

WEDNESDAY, OCTOBER, 6

001. Robustness In STS Research Designs And Methods – Making A Difference In Uncertain Worlds? (part 1)

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

STS has a venerable history in generating theoretical concepts and empirical insights into technology. We pride ourselves in avoiding reductionist accounts and opening the black boxes of technological change. Yet our field struggles to provide comprehensive guidance to academics, practitioners and policy makers in neighboring disciplines. This is particularly salient in domains in which STS seeks not only to critique problematic sociotechnical paradigms but also to intervene around social challenges such as climate change mitigation and democratic participation in innovation and design. We propose that one way to enhance the robustness of STS theories and empirical insights is to rethink dominant research designs and study templates. As sociotechnical change is shaped in many sites and by various social groups, multi-sited studies are needed to allow for the inclusion of actors and modes of knowing rendered invisible by the common investigations of single sites. The uncertainties and contingencies of technological change, in turn, call for longitudinal approaches rather than single snapshot studies. The challenge for STS scholars is how to empirically, methodologically and theoretically “string together” close-up studies of different times and locales with/into broader, longitudinal investigations. Furthermore, how can the insights of these studies be effectively linked to other disciplines and practitioners—who often operate either a more reductionist bird's-eye-view or a piecemeal frog's-eye-view of sociotechnical change? The panel will interrogate these issues from the vantage point of the Biographies of Artifacts and Practices (BoAP) approach that has elaborated a set of tentative responses to the matter.

Participants:

Ethnography at scale: mapping landscapes in depth? *Robin Williams, The University of Edinburgh; Valeri Wiegel, The University of Edinburgh*

Localist ANT & interactionist studies, focused on how social worlds were constituted through processes of bootstrapped induction, have paradoxically fallen into empiricist traps. Despite rich-descriptions of social processes there are issues in unpicking taken-for-granted behaviour and relationships. Reflecting on the failure of interviewees to disclose illegal fixing of LIBOR exchange rates, MacKenzie (2018) has called for historical sociology (based on actor interviews) to be combined with political economy. But how can we develop robust accounts of this kind of broader patterning and framing? BOAP investigations (Hyysalo, Pollock and Williams 2019) have tackled the challenge of identifying taken-for-granted relations by the strategic use of comparison between contrasting settings and over time. Other extensions strategies are possible however. This talk reflects upon an analysis of ethnographic findings collected at industrial scale of the implementation of electronic prescribing systems by a research team embedded in six English hospitals over 3 years. Actor-centric accounts of implementation experience were supplemented by large-scale analysis across the whole fieldwork corpus which brought into view temporal patterns – the gradual emergence of efforts to optimise the capabilities embedded in these complex organisational technologies several years after system go-live – that would not readily have been detected by analysis of actor accounts (Wiegel et al 2019). Digital research methods allowing specific observations to be linked to the original fieldwork setting (e.g. via a recording of an interview) opens up new modes of interpretation and analysis that transcend the polarisation that has beset UK social science between quantitative and qualitative methods.

Long-term configuration of governance and codesign in the creation of digital boundaries: A multi-sited- longitudinal study in a regional ecosystem of care in NHS-England

Andrey M. Elizondo, University of Edinburgh

Experiences like the National Programme for Information Technology (NPfIT) in NHS-England have shown that the characteristics of healthcare industry, plus the scale and complexity of the NHS as organization, makes difficult the creation of one-size-fits-all, nation-wide, centralized digital solutions. After the cancellation of NPfIT in 2012, a laissez-faire of information systems across NHS-England, has contributed to the individual digitalization of care organizations. Diverse stand-alone computer systems have been implemented covering different organizations and segments of the care sector. This flexibility has also increased the multiplicity of systems and reinforced the fragmentation of information. Since 2014, new health policy visions have emphasized not just efficient processing of patients and associated data, but high quality of care by integrating information for supporting entire care pathways. This has created a new impetus to integrate these previously separated systems (primary and secondary care, health and social care, and other services); so separated worlds pulled together around these infrastructures. Avoiding nation-wide projects, such efforts have been promoted across England following a region-wide approach. A complex dynamic of long-term infrastructure construction resulted, in which governance is neither totally top-down, nor totally bottom-up, and the roles of the organizations involved are not totally clear. Focalized in one regional ecosystem, I use BoAP for understanding the multi-sited but also longitudinal condition of this phenomena. The focus of this research lies in understanding the arrangement of actors in the regional ecosystem and the first five years of configuration and evolution of governance and design of a common digital installed-base.

Stringing together case studies of technology development and innovation by subject, time, or topic *Ingo Schulz-Schaeffer, Technical University of Berlin; Martin Meister, TU Berlin; Tim Clausnitzer, Technical University of Berlin; Kevin Wiggert, Technical University of Berlin*

In the discussion about how to string together close-up studies of technology development and innovation, two main strategies have emerged. One strategy is to investigate the development of a particular socio-technical constellation repeatedly in different instantiations. The second strategy is to investigate the subject of interest repeatedly as it evolves over time. Both strategies have been developed and extensively applied by the BoAP research group. In our talk, we want to discuss a variant of the “at different times” strategy and address a third strategy. The variant of the “at different times” strategy is not to follow a particular technology development and innovation process over time but to simultaneously investigate different instantiations of the respective socio-technical constellation at different stages of development. There are examples of this strategy in the corpus of BoAP research but it is still in a nascent stage. Our considerations on this topic will be based on a research design where we investigate the development of human-robot collaboration in different stages of their realization in research laboratories, real-world tests, and real-world applications. The third strategy is to produce continuity and comparability between individual studies not by sticking with a particular subject of research but by sticking with a particular research topic. Our example for illustrating this strategy is sticking with the research question of how prototype scenarios are used in technology development to shape socio-technical constellations, which we first investigated in the field of ubiquitous computing and then applied to technology development in collaborative robotics.

The turn-taking machinery meets actual machines: Linking the detailed study of interactions to the production of facts and artifacts *Ole Pütz, Bielefeld University*

One reason for studying everyday interactions closely is the emergent nature of talk-in interaction. Talk proceeds turn by turn;

each turn being shaped by what was said and at the same time shaping how the conversation continues. It is no exaggeration to say that whatever occurs in an interaction that relies on talk is shaped by this "turn-taking machinery" (Sacks, Schegloff and Jefferson, 1974). But when we extend our focus temporarily to the duration of technoscientific projects, the benefits of snapshot studies that investigate single interactions are less clear. Instead, there are good reasons to call for a string of studies as the BOAP approach does. At the same time, there is a risk of depreciating the investigation of the emergent nature of talk-in interaction before its effects on technoscientific projects are better understood. This paper reassesses why the study of interactions using audio- and video recordings and respective methods of sequential analysis yields insights that cannot be gained using participant observation and taking notes alone. In addition, the paper presents findings from recent work using sequential analysis that suggest that already implemented functionality of prototypes solidifies meanings in talk-in-interaction, a solidification that cannot be observed insofar as potential future functionality is discussed. This finding indicates that the production of artifacts does affect the turn-taking machinery and vice versa, where the indexicality of interaction allows for the exploration of possibilities and artifacts subsequently limit possibilities yet thereby also provide orientation for further explorations.

Beyond 'birth' studies: Linking up multilayered biographies
Alex Christian, University of Edinburgh Business School

STS scholars seem to be particularly well-equipped to study the emergence of a new technology by reconstructing its 'birth' through looking at the various social and technological factors involved in its formation. However, while especially STS scholars influenced by the field of Information Systems may have a tendency to leap from studying the emergence of one new technology to studying the emergence of an even newer and presumptively more interesting technology, important analytical insights can be generated by establishing a theoretical language more apt to examine how already existing technologies may begin to serve a new purpose. Despite acknowledging 'birth' to remain an important 'biographical moment', this paper claims that (over)emphasising the moment of 'birth' as a 'snapshot' may potentially lead to analytically ignoring some of the multiple 'layers' of a technology's biography. To overcome this shortcoming, it is proposed to extend the temporal scope of the BOAP template by throwing light at potentially unstudied, yet critical biographical moments that may occur prior ('pre-natal') or after ('decline' or 'dying' phase) a technology is exposed to public life. In this context, additional analytical value is suggested in revisiting and expanding concepts from various academic disciplines, such as 'repurposing', 'ruination', 'pivot', 'exaptation', 'palimpsest' and 'function creep' to create a taxonomy that enables STS researchers to better account for the plurality and multi-layeredness of a technology's biography. This step would not only help to string together studies from different vantage points but also contribute to more equality in studying the biographies of technologies.

Session Organizers:

Sampsä Hyysalo, Aalto University

Neil Pollock, The University of Edinburgh

David Seibt, Technical University of Berlin

Robin Williams, The University of Edinburgh

002. Conspiracy, Coterie, Contagion And Other Not-so-good Relations

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Goodness is fickle. Goodness is fragile, Martha Nussbaum has argued; and it is potent. Good relations come with agency, legitimacy or care, depending on the moral regime that goodness is inflected in. This panel explores how moralities shape and are shaped in worlds equipped with a

plethora of technologies. The panel focuses on the heterogeneous moralities, brittle and persistent, that animate the mediated, digitized and dated dealings of today. The panel proceeds from the hypothesis that today's technicized worlds re-mix and re-configure regimes of goodness and of engagement (Laurent Thévenot). Digital technologies, Noortje Marres notes, may transform the situational fabric of the everyday, synthesizing public and private in novel ways. Web algorithms, e.g., rank postings and invoke users according to distinct logics of valuation (Andreas Birckbak and Hjalmar Bang Carlsen). When myriad practices are coordinated in far-flung assemblages, public justification, organized planning and intimate care interlock, clash or undermine one another (María Puig de la Bellacasa). Against this backdrop, the panel tends to the weak, wicked, and poor relations that lack agency, legitimacy and care. It examines affected non-users and users (Eric Baumer), bystanders (Susann Wagenknecht), conspirators (Timothy Choy), traitors, trespassers and intruders—shadowy figures that fail to entertain good relations. Drawing attention to bystanding, treason, coterie, contagion (Adam Kramer, Jamie Guillory and Jeffrey Hancock) and carelessness, the panel sets out to tackle a range of uneasy techno-moral figurations.

Participants:

Beyond the carbon weight of cows: exploring desirable futures for cows on dairy farms
Miss Naomi L Hammett, Lancaster University

In this paper I ask what desirable futures might there be for cows that live on dairy farms in North West England? In recent debates relating to climate change, dairy farming has featured as a topic of controversy. Greenpeace (2020), insist that in order to meet climate change targets there needs to be 50% less domesticated animals in the EU and it is claimed that if all humans were to move to vegan diets then vast swathes of land could be rewilded (Poole & Nemecek, 2018), yet what such proposals would mean for the future of dairy cows is rarely considered. In recent decades, practices involving the intermingling of cow bodies with genetic technologies have become commonplace. Cows belonging to breeds commonly used in dairy farming have been described as 'milking machines' (Wicks, 2018) and 'automatons' (Boyde, 2018) where to be such a thing has been viewed as being stripped of agency. As a counter to literature that has a limited and anthropocentric notion of animal agency, Despret (2013) proposes that we consider agency as arising from agencements, that is, a being's ability to respond and be responded to. Using this notion of agency along with the concept of care emerging from feminist STS (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2011) and multispecies justice (Radomska, 2017) I consider through my empirical fieldwork exploring practices on dairy farms in North West England what it might mean to foreground the bodies, lives and futures of cows within research.

Charismatic relationships: the appeal of vaccines' simple and universal solutions and its role in HPV vaccination in Colombia
Natalia Lozano, Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam

This paper argues that charisma is one of the relational forms that relationships among science, technology, and society can take. It explores the making of sociotechnical charismatic relationships at multiple levels by looking at some of the things that the Human Papillomavirus (HPV) vaccine, Gardasil, is enabled to do in the context of Colombian public vaccination for cervical cancer (CC) prevention, where numerous cases of adverse effects have been reported. This way of relating is no right or wrong but is neither natural nor innocent. By constraining meaning making and knowledge production about vaccination injuries, charismatic relationships enact the good things that vaccines do as universal facts. At the same time, it obscures conversations around undesirable experiences and reproduces privilege and oppression. The analysis investigates a diverse assemblage of empirical material gathered through ethnographic research as narratives. These materials include fieldwork notes, interviews' transcripts of girls and young women that reported adverse vaccination effects, policy texts, official reports, academic

papers, and media articles. This paper contributes to STS' discussions on the ambiguous character of sociotechnical promises and the multiple realities that they produce in practice, particularly in the emerging literature on vaccines' science and technology (Meskus and Oikkonen, 2020). It also illustrates the analytical possibilities of exploring processes of co-production of science, technology, and society with the interpretative guidance of charisma (Ames, 2019).

(Not-so-)Good Medicine: The Egghead during the Pandemics
Stefan Nicolae, University of Trier

„A self-conscious prig, so given to examining all sides of a question that he becomes thoroughly addled while remaining always in the same spot“ - this is how the „egghead“ entered the American political scene of the 1950s (Bromfield 1952: 158). Indeed, Louis Bromfield's ‚Triumph of the Egghead‘ became the manifesto of an intense anti-intellectualist attitude (Hofstadter 1962), still present in contemporary debates (Jacoby 2008). While the American public mocks herewith the figure of the „engaged intellectual“ (usually a professor, always an academic), especially German discussions are somehow reluctant to such views. Nevertheless, the ‚egghead‘ has left the background amid the intense debates on expertise and policies during the COVID-19 pandemics in Germany. The ‚egghead‘ irritates: s/he is at the same time a ‚professional‘, a ‚specialist‘ as well as an ‚well-informed citizen‘ (see Schutz 1946), though playing openly none of this roles to the end; as an ‚expert‘, s/he bridges between ‚laymen‘ and ‚decision-makers‘ (Pfadenhauer 2003), though refraining from both common knowledge and political responsibility; as an ‚official advisor‘ s/he praises epidemiological or immunological competences, though questioning their life-worldly relevance. My presentation (re)sketches this particular social figure by looking at its construction in the German media. I argue that the ‚egghead‘ displays a hybrid type of knowledge, structurally resembling Peter L. Berger's and Thomas Luckmann's figure of the ‚expert whose expertise is not wanted by the society at large“ (1966: 143), which reshapes the profile of (scientific and political) expert knowledge.

(Nuclear) neglect neglected: The politics of knowledge production through neglect
Misria Shaik Ali, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

In *The Occupied Clinic*, Varma thinks about good care and “care’s opposites—refusal, neglect, disinterest, and harm” as practiced together when legitimate and shadowy figures care in techno-medico-scientific enactments (13). However, de la Bellacasa in hurriedly offering care practices for “remediating neglect” (162), agnotology scholars in marking off neglect as a psychological and moral issue, and not “as a substantive epistemic practice” as ignorance is (Alcoff 39) and environmental scholars writing in passing about state neglect of contaminated communities and scholars’ and experts’ own neglect of local knowledges about contamination (Ottinger 19), crucial analysis of “neglect” as an epistemic practice that validates, legitimates, enables, and forms epistemologies of matters of concern is itself neglected. Radiation protection rules care for the protection of individuals and environment from irradiation. However, the rules frame the individuals as passive recipients of radioactive dosages rather than as active “agents” of knowing irradiation. Through neglect of their epistemic agency, more-than-human bodies, although “cared for,” and their sensed knowledge about contamination are delegitimized. Neglect shapes legitimate ways of knowing contamination through sensed digital readings of state-sanctioned Geiger counters and environmental surveillance studies. Such legitimate ways of knowing formed through neglect then comes to be “epistemologies of neglect.” Using two contexts of nuclear waste practices—the 2010 Mayapuri radiological incident and the ongoing debate on decommissioning the Indian Point Energy Centre, NY (Ali) – and borrowing from feminist and postcolonial

STS, this paper analyzes “nuclear safety,” a matter of “concern” in nuclear regulation, as an “epistemology of neglect.” In such a way, the paper addresses the techno-moral-epistemic figurations of care/neglect through a sensory, para-sited and multispecies ethnography. Bibliography Alcoff, Linda M. 2008.

“Epistemologies of Ignorance: Three Types.” In *Race and Epistemologies of Ignorance*, 39–58. Charlesbourg, Québec: Braille Jymico Inc. Ali, Misria S. 2020. “Memorializing Decommissioning: A Nuclear Culture Approach to Safety Culture.” *RSA Journal* 31 (2020): 33–58. de la Bellacasa, Maria Puig Matters of Care: Speculative Ethics in More Than Human Worlds. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press. Ottinger, Gwen. 2013. *Refining Expertise: How Responsible Engineers Subvert Environmental Justice Challenges*. New York, NY: New York University Press Varma, Saiba. *The Occupied Clinic Militarism and Care in Kashmir*. Durham: Duke University Press, 2020.

Seed The World, A Common Treasury For All: Digital Media Piracy As Vernacular Technical Tradition
Benjamin Staple, Memorial University of Newfoundland

Called thieves and trespassers, digital media pirates ply the currents of cyberspace, negotiating a dangerous and sometimes ambiguous course between law, morality, and identity. This paper is based on ethnographic research with the former pirate community Kickass Torrents and explores the cultural dimension of digital media piracy as an everyday technical tradition. Lacking legitimacy, pirates collaboratively create their own virtual communities and internal systems of valuation. Within its own techno-moral frame, piracy becomes a “weapon of the weak” (James C. Scott) as pirates practice resistance to laws they perceive to be unjust. In responding to copyright laws, geo-blocking, and socioeconomic conditions, pirates find agency in the illegitimate and illegal. Pirates create themselves through practice and discourse, by the act of infringement and by drawing on traditions of historical maritime piracy and legends of outlaw folk heroes, such as Robin Hood (Shannon Lee Dawdy). Like outlaw folk heroes, pirates are marked by moral ambiguity and ethical relativity (Graham Seal). Through the transgression of national borders and legal boundaries, piracy, by definition, actively fails to maintain good structural relations. Yet, through this transgression, pirates express care and see themselves as working in the public good by offering access to and preservation of otherwise inaccessible art and culture. As content is appropriated and shared within a complex system of social capital, underground pirate economies come to constitute a network-based virtual commons (James Boyle).

Session Organizer:

Susann Wagenknecht, TU Dresden

003. Aspiring Societal Impact. The Epistemological Politics of Interventionist Research in STS - I

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Participants:

On epistemic politics: navigating contested knowledge co-production in action research *Jitse Schuurmans, Erasmus University Rotterdam; Dara Ivanova, Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management; Martijn Felder, Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management; Lieke Oldenhof, Erasmus University, Institute of Health Policy and Management; Iris Wallenburg, institute for Health Policy and Management*

While empirical studies unraveling the epistemic politics in laboratories have formed the bedrock of STS (Doing 2004), there has been less attention for epistemic politics in action research, which is conducted outside the confines of the laboratory. In this paper, we respond to recent calls to investigate the epistemic

politics of action research in the social sciences. A central claim in action research is that knowledge should be co-produced with societal partners in a participatory and democratic process, thereby enabling legitimate and actionable solutions for societal problems (Note of editor 2013; Reason and Bradbury 2008). However, the democratic ideal of knowledge co-production is a highly contested one, due to competing claims about what is considered legitimate expertise. Who is and isn't included in this co-production is therefore a recurring matter of concern (Oldenhof and Wehrens 2018). Moreover, knowledge produced in action-research is not necessarily singular. It can simultaneously materialize into lessons learned in a city lab, a contribution to a debate in an academic journal, and/or a reflexive evaluation report. Action research can therefore be embedded in multiple knowledge(s) and epistemic cultures at the same time (Pickstone 2000). Sometimes these knowledge(s) and cultures complement one another and sometimes they conflict. Drawing on our own work in three national projects in elderly care, social care and nursing, we reflect on our role as action researchers working with and within different knowledge infrastructures. We specifically reflect on and problematize the different kinds of (epistemic) politics in our work as action researchers, foregrounding our contested and often difficult position as nodes in these projects and revealing choices made and their consequences. References P. Doing (2004). 'Lab hands' and the 'Scarlet O'. *Epistemic politics and (scientific) labour. Social Studies of Science*, 34(3), 299–323. Note of editor (2013). Action research: the journal's purpose, vision and mission. *Action Research*, 11(1) 3-7. L.E. Oldenhof & R.L.E. Wehrens (2018). Who is 'in' and who is 'out'? Participation of older persons in health research and the interplay between capital, habitus and field. *Critical Public Health*, Doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/09581596.2018.1435851>. J.V. Pickstone (2000). *Different ways of knowing. A new history of science, technology, and medicine*. University of Chicago Press. P. Reason and H. Bradbury (2008). *The Sage Handbook of action research*. London etc.: Sage Publications.

Creating societal impact *Guus Dix, University of Twente (the Netherlands)*

Impact is a term that is more easily used than defined. It has a long history in the natural sciences where it was closely associated with the way one physical body affects another when they come into contact. Currently, the term predominates in debates about rival idea(l)s of 'excellence' (as in 'Journal Impact Factor') and 'relevance' (as in 'societal impact'). For the panel, I would like to present a research project in the making. That project, Creating Societal Impact (CSI), builds on the double meaning of the verb 'to create'. In a more straightforward sense, creating societal impact covers the wide variety of ways that academics and academic output affects processes and practices outside academia. In a more reflexive sense, creating societal impact covers the coming into being of something that did not exist before, to such an extent or in this particular manner. In that sense, societal impact has been created over the past decade as an object of knowledge and intervention; as something that can be measured, monitored, managed and governed. CSI aims to investigate four intersecting sites and sets of actors that contributed to this creation process: European policymakers who put technological innovation first; universities who, as strategic actors, try to reinvent themselves as creators of impact; scientometricians who develop and sell impact-oriented measurement tools; and research groups in the social and behavioral sciences that (fail to) develop the kinds of research practices that enable them to do good in terms of the new realities of impact.

The Paradox of Publically Engaged Research - Scientific Authority, Self-Reflection and Problematization in the German Coal Phase Out *Jeremias Herberg, Institute for Science in Society, Radboud University*

In this contribution we present reflections and empirical findings from our scholarly and transdisciplinary engagement with the social consequences of the coal phase out in the East German Region of Lusatia. In working with civic initiatives, large industries and policy makers we have encountered three paradoxes which are characteristic for engaged research: 1) The paradox of scientific authority (Bijker et al. 2009; Eyal 2019) takes on a particularly dynamic development in transdisciplinary collaborations. Committed scholars are called upon to participate in the design process, but at the same time they are often criticised for doing so. 2) A paradox of reflection becomes apparent: The public role of science often includes the expectation that it should create transformative impacts on the one hand, and that it needs to re-think and control its agency and positionality on the other. 3) The paradox of problematization is the most complex challenge to engaged researchers. In transformation processes and public conflicts, engaged research are expected to offer policy solutions, but even the problematization of socioecological and sociotechnical changes can intricately deeply involve scholars in public debates and site-specific controversies. The German coal phase out, which we have studied for three years by means of ethnographic approaches and interpretative policy analysis, is a fitting case study: Environmental pressures, inherited inequities, populist tendencies and innovation policies shape the affected regions. It follows that the authority, reflexive capacity and problematization, which social scientists come up with, is likely to bear unexpected consequences and heated controversies. We discuss ethnographic accounts and policy processes that exemplify those paradoxes, while proposing sociological concepts and transdisciplinary practices that help to tackle them.

Doing Positive Health, doing engaged STS research *Gili Yaron, Health Services Research, Faculty of Health, Medicine and Life Sciences, University Maastricht; Marieke Spreeuwenberg, Maastricht University, Health Services Research; Dirk Ruwaard, Maastricht University, Health Services Research*

Despite ongoing debates on health concepts and their role in healthcare policy and practice (Huber et al 2011, Leonardi 2018, Haverkamp, Bovenkerk & Verweij 2018), there is a dearth of empirical studies on this subject. In this paper, I will present the findings of our action-oriented study into the introduction of a novel, comprehensive health concept called 'Positive Health' (PH) in the Netherlands. PH is currently being taken up with gusto in Dutch healthcare, but also in social work, governance, housing, and education. Despite the scientific connotations of the term 'health concept', our study demonstrates that PH is much more than a theoretical construct. Indeed, this concept can be understood as a soft type of "sticky technology" (Scott-Smith 2018) that adheres to various usages and contexts. Gaining and losing shape in ongoing, shifting interactions between different fields, PH nevertheless retains a recognizable identity. All the while, various stakeholders (policy makers, practitioners, researchers) use it to pursue different goals. PH is mobilized in five interconnected though not necessarily harmonious ways: as a multidimensional health model, an instrument for reflection upon individuals' experienced health, an organizational innovation, a framework for transdisciplinary collaboration, and a social movement. Strikingly, by presenting this typical STS analysis and resultant recommendations to the field, we as researchers co-shape and mobilize the concept ourselves. I will therefore conclude the paper by discussing the meaning of doing engaged research for the field, the concept under study, and our own role and position as STS-researchers.

Session Organizer:

Jitse Schuurmans, Erasmus University Rotterdam

Chair:

Dara Ivanova, Erasmus School of Health Policy and

Management

Discussants:

Iris Wallenburg, Institute for Health Policy and Management
Roland Bal, Erasmus University Rotterdam

004. Critical and Reflexive Perspectives on Conferencing as Scientific Practice - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Academic conferences are prime sites of exchange in global science. As events where face-to-face or digital encounters occur, they represent important nodes of knowledge circulation, and serve as spaces of research communication, academic identity formation, and networking. 'Conferencing' is recognised as an essential activity for building an academic career, which is manifested through the inclusion of conference participation and organisation in recruitment and promotion criteria. Conference participation, however, frequently requires access to resources that are distributed highly unequally – such as funding, visas, work-place permission, family support, and freedom from care responsibilities for the duration of an event. As such, academic conferences are sites of privilege and disadvantage, which may reinforce social inequalities in relation to gender, nationality, race/ethnicity, social class/caste, disability, language, and other intersecting dimensions of difference. This panel critically interrogates conferencing as scientific practice and its structuring effects in academia. It comprises contributions that offer theoretical conceptualisations, empirical studies and critical reflections on conference practices and their impact on maintaining/reproducing inequalities in the scientific field. Despite growing interest in conferences and an expanding evidence base revealing their adverse social and environmental effects, they remain a niche subject in the social studies of science. The panel seeks to provide an integrative discursive space to stimulate the formation of a scholarly network for future exchange, linking STS with higher education research and gender studies. The panel consists of two sessions, whereby this first one focuses on conferencing as academic practice - in fictional and real world settings.

Participants:

What 'Counts' In (Forest) Science? Examining Conferences As Spaces of Academic Valuation Practice *Susanne Koch*,
Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University

Despite their significance for individual and collective research trajectories, conferences still represent an underexplored terrain of science studies. I address this gap by examining them as spaces in which academic valuation is practised and performed. Therefore, I build on two strands of scholarship: From science studies, I take that researchers' position in a scientific field substantially depends on peer recognition and the ascription of scientific authority by members of the respective community. Valuation studies, on the other hand, offer insights how worth and value are ascribed in academic settings. I link these research areas to investigate valuation processes in the context of scientific conferences which have so far hardly received attention. To examine such processes empirically, I focus on academic events in the interdisciplinary field of forest science. The knowledge it delivers informs policymaking in various sectors and scientific forestry worldwide. A substantial part of it, however, is generated by (predominantly male) scholars based in the Global North. This manifests also in the conference space where women and scholars from Southern world regions are under-represented particularly in roles with decision-making and gate-keeping power. In this paper, I explore how selection and valuation practices contribute to maintaining such asymmetries. Drawing on ethnographic methods, I show how value is ascribed to certain groups of scholars and types of forest research on stage and backstage of conference events. Presenting insights from an exploratory study, my paper also includes methodological considerations how value construction in 'live' interaction of academics can be grasped.

Conferencing as networking practice – chances, challenges and evening beers *Jennifer Dahmen-Adkins*, *RWTH Aachen University*; *Astrid Schulz*, *RWTH Aachen University*; *Andrea Wolffram*, *RWTH Aachen University*

Participation in and presenting papers at conferences are an integral part of the professional socialisation of scientists. They are places of networking, knowledge exchange and establishing and maintaining one's own visibility within the scientific community; thus, they provide the opportunity to increase one's social capital and related potential resources. In this paper networking practices of PostDocs and gatekeepers, like professors, in the field of engineering and information technology are going to be presented with a special focus on their descriptions of conferences as opportunity structures for developing connections with relevant actors. The utterances of younger researchers reflect the importance of such meetings for their careers, but also describe the significance of informal moments like conference dinners, coffee breaks and casual get togethers. But what does it need to be included in such occasions, what role do their superiors play in introducing them to the community and in sharing relevant tacit knowledge? The statements of both interviewed groups offer the possibility to draw conclusions about the extent to which conferences as a scientific practice besides offering potential opportunities also can represent spaces of exclusion and (gendered) injustice. The paper will close with recommendations for institutional measures, which can support more just opportunities of conference attendances especially for young researchers in depending positions.

Gender and the Symbolic Power of Academic Conferences in Fictional Texts *Pauline Reynolds*, *University of Redlands*; *Emily Henderson*, *University of Warwick*

Across the contemporary global higher education sector, there is an increased focus on gendered inequalities in the academic profession. Previous studies construct a clear picture of the academy as an unfriendly profession for women, particularly highlighting their challenge to 'belong'. A growing body of literature demonstrates how conferences contribute to the development of academic careers but are also shown to be exclusionary spaces for many different groups, including women academics. This presentation focuses on conferences as a contributor to inequalities in the academic profession by exploring the role of cultural representations of conferences – and the academics involved. Based on a qualitative gender analysis of symbolic references to academic conferences in a corpus of narrative fiction texts, this presentation examines the extent to which fictional representations of conferences reinforce and exacerbate gender inequalities in the academy. Focusing on who is attending fictional conferences and what these characters are doing at or in relation to conferences, our analysis highlights the ways that fictional conferences serve as terrain to establish and contest authentic academic subjectivities related to gender. We argue that cultural representations of academics cannot be ignored in gender analyses of academia, due to the role that cultural representations play in constructing a dominant imaginary of authentic academic subjectivity.

Session Organizers:

Susanne Koch, Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University
Emily Henderson, University of Warwick
Nidhi Sadana Sabharwal, National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (India)

Chair:

James Burford, La Trobe University

005. The Post-Truth age: What is this really about? - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Debates on 'post truth' have become a visible staple of recent STS, the word having gathered media and journalistic attraction — though mostly in the Anglosphere — to include discussions and commentaries in some of the main journals in the field such as *Social Studies of Science and Engaging Science, Technology and Society*. However, most papers and books published on the subject of 'post truth' (within and outside STS) are presented in the form of essays or reflections that are based on little or no firsthand systematic, empirical research, and with limited geographic diversity. In this panel, we propose to bring together STS scholars interested in debating what it means to live in a post-truth age — if we are indeed living in such a new age at all — based on empirical studies. Thus, while 'post truth' is most commonly associated with the idea that contemporary societies have entered a period in which facts matter less to public opinion than emotions and personal beliefs, there remains much to be worked out in terms of what, in this respect, distinguishes the current age from others. In this panel we seek to bring together papers based on research that seeks to either rectify or destabilize a taken-for-granted, definitive and universalist definition of 'the post-truth age', based on evidence of changes to contemporary societies, in a wider variety of contexts, which would justify adopting such an all-embracing concept.

Participants:

A Contextual Examination of Factuality on Social Media
Anushree Gupta, IIT Hyderabad; Tarunima Prabhakar, Tattle Technologies

The post-truth era is co-located with the rise of social media. Facebook's partnership with International Fact-Checking Network (IFCN) affiliated fact-checking organizations in 2016 marked a pivotal event in this era. Facebook clarified that the partnership would only target intentional hoaxes while excluding claims from politicians or partisan disputes. "The worst of the worst" posts were eligible to be adjudicated against facts. This partnership was an admittance to a regulatory ideal of non-subjectivity, for at least a selection of posts. Other platforms followed suit in partnering with 'third-party fact checkers' certified by IFCN, making IFCN guidelines an indispensable infrastructure for content moderation on social media. Interrogating this infrastructure then enables us to trace the emerging boundary of a 'fact' on social media. We do this by tracing the geographical and political context in which IFCN emerged (political campaigning in the US) and contrast it with the social, political, and material realities of social media users outside that context. In particular, we share findings from annotating claims in social media posts from one such context in the Global South. Reflecting on our process of annotating 2200 posts from an Indian social media platform, we ask- what is the modality of a claim in multimedia user-generated content? We aim to show that the aesthetic and modality of content bears on what is considered to be a claim and ultimately a question of fact. This opens avenues to reclaim media artifacts from the terrain of post-truth, into the boundaries of factuality.

Digital divide and fake news – the failure of vaccination campaign in Bulgaria.
Ivaylo Georgiev Yoshkov, Sofia University "St. Kliment Ohridski"

The development of information and communication technologies (ICT) is causing economic, social and cultural transformations that impacts different societies. Various explanations define the phenomenon of the digital divide: some of them describe the gap between those that have access to digital technologies and those that do not (Monge, Chacón) while others argue that framing the digital divide as a technological problem and as a matter of adoption, means to ignore other variables such as the overall socio-cultural, educational and political background (Ragnedda, Vartanova, Gladkova). The second level of the digital division includes the so-called known as media literacy (Vinueza) - skills such as the ability to find reliable information, recognize insecure sites, the ability to solve common problems online, etc. According to the European commission's Digital economy and society index 2020 only 28%

of Bulgarian adults have at least basic digital skills. This study analyzes the ways in which digital divide facilitates the spread of fake news about covid-19 and how this affects the beliefs of different groups regarding the vaccination campaign in Bulgaria. For this purpose, publications and users' comments from both official and anonymous online media websites in the country are selected and subjected to qualitative content analysis. The analysis covers 10 days before and 10 days after the start of the vaccination campaign. The results outline ways to improve access to real news by increasing media literacy and using online tools to verify sources.

Ignorance as Power: Telegram, Covid-19 and the Co-production of Truth in Brazil under Bolsonaro
Paulo F C Fonseca, UFBA; Leonardo Fernandes Nascimento, Federal University of Bahia; Juciane Pereira de Jesus, Universidade Federal da Bahia; Jéffe Batista, UFBA

Since its election, Brazil's president Jair Bolsonaro has promoted a specific culture for politics and policy-making, in which the production, diffusion and control of ignorance is a crucial governmental strategy. This has been particularly visible in the unfolding of the COVID-19 crisis in Brazil, when federal government government has insisted in a controversial agenda that ignores sound health and policy science. In this paper, we contribute to the empirical investigation of what has been called of post-truth age through an in-depth study of how the controversies over the treatment and immunization for COVID-19 are framed and structured within pro-bolsonaro Telegram groups. The research draws on a software-assisted analysis of digital data (text and audio) from Telegram Instant Messenger Platform. We analyze all Covid-19 messages between March 1st 2020 and June 30th 2021 from a Bolsonaro supporters' Telegram group with more than 14,000 participants. Based on the analysis of this sample, we dissect the discursive path of some of the politico-scientific controversies around the Brazilian central government's approach to the pandemic to understand the role of digital militancy in these practices. Through mixed methods of digital social research, we characterize the multi-platform media ecosystem of legitimating content, as well as some of the strategies for the institutionalization of ignorance and the exclusion of specific uncomfortable knowledges through boundary work. Based on our findings, we shed light on how the dispute over 'what to ignore' permeates science and the State and discuss its implications for models of democratic governance and public accountability.

The 'Gender Ideology' and the Peace Referendum in Colombia:
 Post-truth and Reflexive Challenges for STS
Javier Guerrero-C, Instituto Tecnológico Metropolitano

On October 2, 2016, Colombians voted in a referendum on a peace agreement between the government and the FARC, the strongest and oldest left-wing guerrilla force. The peace accord was narrowly rejected by 50.2%. The 'No' campaign managed to mobilize historic hatred for the guerrillas, fear of the left ("Colombia will become another Venezuela") along with a now-familiar mixture of right-wing cultural themes, including homophobia, anti-feminism, and resistance to gender equality, encompassed in the term 'gender ideology' which the right used as a motto. As in the near-simultaneous UK Brexit referendum and the USA Trump election, much of this campaign was conducted on social media. In this chapter, I explore, using digital methods (Vertesi et al., 2019), the relationship between social media and political rhetoric in Colombia's post-conflict and post-truth politics. At the same time, and reflexively, I investigate the challenges for STS when using digital methods (Marres, 2017) and I engage with the post-truth age's digital and infrastructural materialities to understand the role of algorithms and social media (primarily Twitter and Facebook) in the spread of the gender ideology trope, after and prior to the peace referendum in Colombia. Finally, I reflect on the reflexive

challenges faced by a field whose commitments emphasize the contingent and constructed nature of facts when attempting to produce a more public and active role for itself in the context of political polarization in Colombia.

Session Organizer:

Tiago Ribeiro Duarte, University of Brasília

006. Crip Use

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

In her recent book, *What's the Use?*, feminist philosopher Sara Ahmed offers the concept of for-ness to describe the phenomenological relationality of use, the subject's turning in the direction of an object in a dynamic of intersubjectivity, or what Merleau-Ponty called "intentionality." Ahmed applies for-ness to feminist theories of use and usefulness, showing the justice-centered stakes of orienting-toward as a form of use. This roundtable of disabled scholars and artists begins with Ahmed's notion of for-ness to theorize use in the context of crip technoscience and disability access. Ahmed's position of for-ness in relation to "use," we will show, allows us to expand the range of questions it is possible to ask about access as good relation: for what political purposes, for which disabled and sick bodies, and toward what interpersonal and institutional relations is the phenomenon we call access? When the body is a boundless, leaky container, can it be a legible recipient of for-ness? Can beginning with the concept of for-ness compel a distinction between forms of access aimed at productivity and assimilation and those for anti-normative and anti-assimilationist collaborations? Can for-ness make sense of the contradictions inherent in the concept of "access-for-all," when some forms of access produce exclusion for other users?

Presenters:

Aimi Hamraie, Vanderbilt University

Kelsie Acton, unknown

Josh Halstead, ArtCenter College of Design

Session Organizer:

Jarah Moesch, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute - STS

007. The Covid-19 Pandemic as a Test of STS Knowledge and Lessons

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

The Covid-19 pandemic is unparalleled in modern history on both the political and scientific fronts. The only comparable event, the Spanish flu, did not entail the measures of exception such as lockdowns and curfews that we have been witnessing since March 2020. Nor was it accompanied by a similar foregrounding of scientific debate and scrutiny of every scientific or medical pronouncement. The origin and characteristics of SARS-CoV-2, screening tests, medicines and treatments, fatality rates, masks, vaccines, all have turned into issues hotly debated in the public sphere, both at the national and international levels. On the surface the pandemic seems to conform to the controversial dynamics of knowledge production and use emphasized by STS in the last four decades or so. From this observation, the premise of the panel is that the outbreak and management of Covid-19 provides us with a unique opportunity to test our widely held conclusions on various dimensions of the science/politics interface. Given that normative and public policy concerns clearly pervade a number of STS works, one may also interrogate the extent to which various Covid actors behave according to the lessons taught by the field. The problem of whether Covid-19 vindicates and/or challenges STS knowledge and principles can be addressed by investigating at least three thematic clusters. 1. Risk societies and scientific uncertainty. 2. Controversies and scientific consensus formation. 3. Public engagement in science and conspiracy hunting.

Participants:

Crisis Of Agency: Exploring The Subjectivities Of The UK Covid-19 Digital Contact Tracing App **Danial Naqvi**, *The University of Manchester*

The Covid-19 global pandemic has created disjunctures with prevalent epistemic authorities such as scientists and

government. In attempts to map rising infections, the UK government commissioned the development of a digital contact tracing app. First by Apple and Google, which the NHS digital team, NHSx, finished; the app served as a vehicle for public debate on privacy, civil liberties, and agency. This paper identifies the different subjectivities encountered through the techno-material possibility of a digital contact tracing app. Using a novel approach of YouTube comments and a composite narrative analytical frame, this paper finds three personalities who engage and resist the idea of the app. First, the cynic assumes a sarcastic and fatalistic disposition that insults or makes jokes about other actors. Second, the diplomat resorts to facts-based inquiry of the app to show genuine support or concern for the endeavour. Third, the prophet likens to the 'conspiracy theorist' who mistrusts the establishment and displays self-reliance through warnings to others. Using themes of trust, surveillance, and consent, this paper finds that each character demonstrates a unique orientation to the app, which deserve attention for public engagement, science communication, and future political projects. This paper contributes an empirical example of the importance of treating publics' opinions with care and valuing emotions as constitutive of communicating experimental innovation in times of national crisis. The results of this paper demonstrate that STS must engage with social media methods to investigate social transformation in a hyper-mobile world.

Epistemic Authority in the COVID-19 Pandemic: The Case of Turkey

Zubeyde Demircioglu, *Istanbul Medeniyet University*

As an epistemic crisis, the pandemic is a period in which uncertainty increases and expert knowledge gains importance. Due to its rapidly spreading nature many questions about the disease remained unanswered. Despite the scientific uncertainty and lack of scientific consensus, countries have had to adopt various strategies to make public decisions. In the case of Turkey, the Turkish government established The Coronavirus Scientific Advisory Board (Koronavirüs Bilim Kurulu) on January 10, 2020, which included 26 medical scientists with expertise in pulmonology, infectious diseases, clinical microbiology, and a legal adviser and the Health Minister of Turkey as chairman. As the science advisor, the Board enables policymakers to choose the best policies. Besides, the Board ensures communication between state and citizens to communicate and adopt public policies. Due to its commitment to the government, controversies aroused about the capacity to generate independent opinions and reliability of data. In this context, this study will focus on Scientific Advisory Board of Turkey. First, the study will build a timeline tracking key events and decisions of national pandemic policy. Then it will focus on how the Scientific Advisory Board constructed as the epistemic authority in a discursive context at the early phase of the pandemic. It will discuss the nature of communication between the board and citizens, how the Board presents expert knowledge, scientific uncertainties, and controversies. Finally, it will examine how the public responds to the Board's expert advice.

Sociologizing "Fake News". Discussing the Theory of Misinformation

Valeria Gisell Sánchez Prieto, *Pontificia Universidad Javeriana*; **Juan Camilo Ospina Deaza**, *Pontificia Universidad Javeriana*

Nowadays most of the people from private and public organizations focused on the importance of "read truthful and dependable information" and "do not believe on those malicious fake news" in order to "really understand" what is going on in the scientific, power, and the media field. It is believed that the world information about the presidential campaigns, and the COVID-19 research is usually misunderstood because "people do not look in the right sources". However, what some entities are forgetting is that the problem is not about, if there is enough information about a topic, but the accessibility to know some kind of information depends on people social conditions of

existence, and also on how the information is disseminate. Human beings are not like USB devices in which information A is transmitted to subject B identically, but it implies appropriation, analysis and adaptation to particular contexts. We would like to discuss, from the perspective of social studies of science and sociology of information, the production of “fake news”, the skills people need to comprehend the information, and how misinformation theory is, in fact, a moral theory of the world which try to establish what is true or lie, who are the people of knowledge and the ignorant ones, what could give us trust and allow us to make decisions, and what could cause distrust and incentivize uncertainty. This exercise of believing it is possible to know “the one true of the world” is causing censorship because what is setting aside are the points of view of population. Who can be silenced and who cannot? How to choose who has that power? Although the emphasis on technology, innovation and social media is important, it is necessary not to fetishize these instruments as if by themselves they generate social change.

The Covid-19 Pandemic as a Factor Promoting Consensus and Universalism in STS *Eve Seguin, UQAM*

From their inception, STS have emphasized multiplicity and diversity in the domain that was allegedly most cohesive: science. By treating minority views as worth of study in their own terms rather than as deviation from orthodoxy, controversy studies have given them visibility and even a form of respectability. One side effect of the symmetry principle was thus to give STS the appearance of being politically oriented towards the losing side and the underdogs of the history of science. This observation led some scholars to motivate STS to openly adopt a stance in favour of the weak. This call seems to have been variously heard in STS quarters. Feminist and postcolonial studies, for instance, are seemingly devoted to minority practices of reality production that otherwise would not cross the boundaries of their domain. These studies seem motivated by an awareness of injustice, and the determination to redress the balance and give credit to minority knowledges vis à vis modern science. In a related yet more abstract fashion, empirical studies of ontology claim that we should cease to attend to chosen realities and devote our attention to the practices that produce shadowy, not quite realized beings in the margins. Hence for quite a long time, “it could be otherwise” has been the STS motto. Through the identification and analysis of STS papers, commentaries, editorials and other discursive productions related to Covid-19, we will try to assess whether the pandemic may have curbed STS towards consensus, universalism, and institutionalization.

The work of coming to concepts: Arriving at a singular story of COVID-19 in East Arnhem Land *Michaela Spencer, Charles Darwin University*

This presentation reflects on a piece of collaborative research carried out by the Ground Up research team at Charles Darwin University, Australia during the early stages of COVID-19. Sharing accounts of their own experiences of COVID-19 in communities and clan estates across Arnhem Land, Yolŋu Aboriginal Australian members of this research team contrasted government public health practices with Yolŋu ways of enacting bodies, collective safety and governance in a crisis. In doing so, they helped some of the vibrant multiplicities of COVID-19 become visible to broader academic and public health audiences. When reflecting on this work again now, there is an easy analogy which might be drawn between these stories from the Yolŋu researchers, and Annemarie Mol’s work revealing the complex multiplicity of the disease atherosclerosis (2001). However, in revealing these complex multiplicities, the Yolŋu team were NOT challenging the value or possibility of a singular concept of COVID-19. To the contrary, they recognise that singular working stories are crucial, but that they need to be arrived at through appropriate processes of negotiation and collectively coming to

agreement. It is this sometimes-overlooked aspect of theorising which remains in focus here.

„Trust the expert – Information sources and compliance with ongoing CoVid-19 restrictions“ *Carla Schieb, Institut für Kommunikationswissenschaft; Hannah Lorenz, Muenster University; Sam Fujarski, Muenster University; Bernd Bloebaum, Muenster University; Volker Gehrau, Muenster University*

The aim of the present study is to compare compliance with SARS-CoV-2 preventive actions during two measurement dates in 2020. While it is well documented that compliance rates are high in early times of health crises (Kuiper et al., 2020) and that they are related to perceived susceptibility, institutional trust (trust in media, trust in health experts and scientists, and trust in politicians), and extensive information seeking behavior (Austin et al., 2012), less is known about how these factors differ during an ongoing pandemic. Evidence for “pandemic fatigue” (Reicher & Drury, 2021), meaning a decline in aforementioned factors in long-term crisis situations, emerged in the form of growing mistrust during the H1N1 pandemic (Bangerter et al., 2012). We conducted two representative online surveys in early May 2020 and in late November 2020 with roughly 650 respondents each in Germany, aged 18 to 80 years. In order to improve response rates among older respondents, random digit dialing CAT-interviews were conducted additionally. Most notably, our findings suggest compliance with measures despite the pandemic’s dynamics, except from lower social distancing rates in November, possibly indicating “pandemic fatigue”. Furthermore, we find vital importance of traditional media use (TV, radio, and newspapers) which remains stable at each instant, but we observe ambiguity towards trust in journalists and media coverage of the pandemic. Rather than trust in politicians, we found trust in health experts to be a significant predictor of compliance with pandemic restrictions, therefore signaling the importance of both crisis communication and science communication.

Session Organizer:

Eve Seguin, UQAM

Chair:

Pinna Geraldine Abir-Am, Brandeis University

Discussant:

Warwick Anderson, University of Sydney

008. Centering Public Healthcare I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Though healthcare provides fundamental conditions of (im)possibility for life in the places we research, the workings of public (socialized, employment-based, welfare state) healthcare often remain both allusive and elusive in the studies of science, technology, and medicine (STM). While conceiving of healthcare provision, access, and policy as underlying analyses of biomedical knowledge production, patient-doctor relationships, and illness subjectivities, we seldom explore in depth the co-constitutive forces of the knowledges, practices, and technologies involved in producing, operating, maintaining, and transforming public healthcare. Healthcare structures index particular histories, ethics, and ideologies. They represent a foundational politics of life baked into institutions, pre-structuring care relationships, and organizing social life and membership. They can be a source of stability, solidarity, and social prosperity, much as they generate gaps and uncertainties, strategic ignorances and bureaucracies of exclusion. We invite fellow STM scholars to help us develop better vocabulary, methods, and theories for understanding and analyzing practices of administering and the administration of public healthcare.

Participants:

Approximations: Collective Health & Sociotechnical Metonymy in São Paulo *Jack Mullee, University of Chicago, Department of Anthropology*

In Brazil, universal public healthcare is backed by the sciences of “collective health” (saúde coletiva), the Brazilian offshoot of “Latin American social medicine” that emerged in the mid-1970s under conditions of military dictatorship. Since the return to democracy (1985) and the inclusion of the “right to health” in a new Constitution (1988), collective health has been variously institutionalized in university curricula and public policy at all scales of government. In this paper, I explore the technics of collective health as they were articulated by scientists in São Paulo, Brazil’s largest city, in the wake of the fall of the leftist Rouseff government in 2016. Worried about conservative threats to “dismantle” the universal health system (“SUS”), collective health scientists (“sanitaristas”) concluded that their technoscience had become out of step with society. In response, sanitaristas sought to reinvigorate their science and their movement by reconceptualizing the technicity of “the social” itself. I show that reflexive critiques of collective health were usually calibrated to scalar and situational metonyms of the social (e.g. the neighborhood, the crowd, the municipality, the everyday, the user) such that the theater of health technopolitics was thought to be located in ever-more-granular nooks and crannies of social experience. With special implications for the megacity context of São Paulo, this paper calls attention to the ways that universal health technicities are concretized through the material semiotics of (metropolitan) social life.

Entanglements of pain and relief: A critical look at palliative care in Kerala, India *Nishanth Kunnukattil Shaji, Department of Science and Technology Studies, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute*

Kerala’s Palliative Care Movement is a grassroots initiative that provides free palliative care to people through a network of volunteers, local self-governing institutions (the state), and civil society at large. As a movement, it thrives on the rhetoric of a de-medicalized form of care that lends credence and value to the ‘social’ side of care. Through three central nodes of analysis, this paper seeks to analyse the multiple entanglements that structure the administration of palliative care in the state of Kerala. First, I look at how Kerala’s largely successful state-led healthcare system and its reliance on Local and Self-Governing Institutions (LSGIs), together with an ever-increasing presence of privately run community-based organizations (CBOs) structure the provision of palliative care in the State. Second, I focus on how ideas of identity and community, interpellated by local, cultural and historical factors, play out in the context of the provision of care. Finally, I turn to the use and reliance on multiple medical technologies that make up the material world of care delivery that primarily include painkillers but are also inclusive of medical devices for assisted living such as catheters, feeding tubes, anti-decubitus mattresses, and cleaning solutions. Their production, distribution, and administering quantity are pushed through intricate yet varying webs of legality and bureaucracy. The paper argues that this last technoscientific dimension is often overlooked and impinges far more strongly on the concept of ‘total pain’ (Clark 1999) in which palliative care is emplaced.

Participation Under Maintenance: on (not) Holding Together a Common Ground in Participatory Public Healthcare *Fenna Smits, University of Amsterdam*

In the Netherlands, as elsewhere in European welfare states, the participation of local communities in the decision-making and delivery of public services promises a democratic and locally fitting alternative to institutionalised healthcare. While social scientists frequently evaluate acts of participation in terms of democratic innovation, how acts of participation stabilise in durable infrastructures of communal health is often left unattended. This paper argues that to assess how participation in public healthcare delivers its promises in practice, sociologist should also study what happens after democratic innovation. Through an analytical lens of maintenance this paper asks how

attempts at communal healthcare unfold and (do not) hold in day to day participation practices. I present an ethnographic case study of ongoing attempts to maintain a communal infrastructure of public healthcare in the rural north of the Netherlands and attend in ethnographic detail to the maintenance of three communal goods: the maintenance of responsibility, the maintenance of expertise, and the maintenance of community. By zooming in on a controversy about what constitutes ‘good care’, the case study demonstrates how maintenance practices of local residents creatively open up institutionalised definitions of what constitutes care and a healthy community, but have trouble in stabilising a durable common ground. Moreover, I show that precisely what is common, and to whom, in health care is in constant flux and a fragile, temporary, attainment. In doing so, I expose the precarious and laborious work involved in maintaining a common ground for public health goods.

Saving Money, Saving Lives: The Long Fight for Public Access to Trans- Therapeutics *Christoph Hansmann, San Francisco State University*

This presentation discusses how a coalition of activists, advocates, and care providers in New York City intervened on notions of risk and solidarity to demand public funding for transgender therapeutics. These were formally excluded from state Medicaid funding for seventeen years, but in 2015, this coalition successfully overturned the exclusion. As part of a larger project on transgender health activism and care provision in the United States and Argentina, the presentation analyzes how an activist coalition appropriated and refashioned the “three aims” of population health: care equity, prevention, and cost-savings. Working with and against austerity politics, they successfully contested long-standing claims by state administrators and popular media that trans- therapeutics are too specialized, politicized, or expensive for public financing. Based on ethnographic data, activist materials, and regulatory documents, I show how New York-based activists mobilized statistics to foreground how structural violence and inequity shape trans- health care provision and outcomes. The presentation centers a two-year campaign in New York that strove to redefine trans- therapeutics not as an illegitimate public burden but instead as a common-sense approach to social care writ large. I show how activists and advocates used statistical collectivization to reverse the Medicaid exclusion and to reframe notions of actuarial solidarity (Ewald 2020). Drawing on Murphy’s (2017) “economization of life” and Patel’s (2006) concerns with “risky subjectivity” (2006), I will discuss the intended and unintended effects of the campaign. More broadly, I will argue for the methodological necessity of STS engagements with public infrastructures of health.

Session Organizers:

Shoshana Deutsh, Cornell University

Lisa Lehner, Cornell University

009. Citizen Science as Method - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Participants:

Developing good methods after Fukushima *Yasuhito Abe, Komazawa University*

This paper examines the role of method in shaping citizen science after the Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Disaster of 2011. While multiple and different scholars have discussed and investigated the role of citizens in shaping data on radioactive contamination for the past 10 years with a particular focus upon people and technology, little has been known about the role of method in shaping their citizen science practices. Indeed, method is likely to be less visible than data and sensors. In order to validate any scientific claim, it is thus fundamentally important to communicate methods to audiences in an effective way. This

paper sheds light upon the rhetorical role of method in differentiating a citizen science practice from other citizen sensing practices after Fukushima. More specifically, this study examines how Minna no Date Site (or Collective Database of Citizen's Radioactivity Measurement Labs, MDS) constructed and communicated its data production method to its target audience in a historical context. MDS is one of the most active grassroots citizen science projects in Japan and effectively explains its data production method for the general audiences. Based on textual analysis and ethnography, this paper examines the development of MDS's data production method in relation to other methods, and highlights the rhetorical role of method in shaping MDS as a case of citizen science practice in Japan. In doing so, this paper seeks to contribute to the fields of citizen science and citizen sensing research and communication studies in Japan and elsewhere.

Finding The Right Pole and Hiding In Plain Sight - Radiation Monitoring In Fukushima *Louise Elstow, Lancaster University*

In this paper I share two examples of what is involved in 'making and doing' citizen science from the perspective of one group of citizens doing radiation monitoring in Fukushima after the 2011 nuclear disaster. The first highlights considerations for siting a new sensor near the Fukushima Dai-ichi nuclear power plant and deliberations about the right pole to use. The correct pole it transpires is one to which multiple owners might have a claim, thus making it likely no one owner would mind or even notice an additional sensor being attached. The second example concerns discussions about the right method of putting up stickers that state local radiation levels in public spaces, for individuals who have no access to online radiation maps. Examined in more detail these two cases demonstrate that the methods used by citizen scientists for making and sharing their data incorporate decisions about and a balancing act between, being overt and covert. Citizens do not always have the same access to the locations where data gathering needs to take place as formal institutions. My research suggests that to overcome this, citizen science methods incorporate a degree of remaining visible, whilst incorporating practices that promote tactical hiding. Various workarounds were employed to make use of visible bureaucratic tendencies to enable the devices to remain camouflaged and therefore undisturbed. The group I worked with were able to take advantage of elements of Japanese culture to allow them to 'hide in plain sight'.

The social life of citizen science as method *Alexandra Albert, University College London*

The practices and processes of citizen science contribute to debates around the social life of methods – that is, the 'exploration of the changing historical boundaries between the implicit and the explicit, and the mechanisms and devices which can produce formal knowledge' (Savage 2013, p. 18). This paper focuses more specifically on how the method of citizen science plays out in the discipline of social science, and conceptualises and frames it in the context of a renewal of interest in the politics of method. Studying methods raises fundamental theoretical questions about the limits of knowledge itself (Savage 2013). The real learning comes in the social life of the method – in the practice of the thing – since from here, social innovation springs (Ochu, 2014). Such a positioning revisits the crisis of imagination (Gane 2012) where the fetishisation of readymade quantitative and qualitative methods in social science is more apparent now than it was when Mills wrote *The Sociological Imagination* in the late 1950s. Citizen social science challenges top-down approaches to data collection and generation (Albert, 2021), potentially providing alternative research questions and an opportunity for sharing a diversity of interpretations or acknowledging different situated knowledges (Haraway, 1998). Citizen social science generates and engages in reflections on the politics of knowledge production, giving rise to questions around

what counts as data, who can collect it, and how it can be used (Albert, 2021) and making methods the object of enquiry (Savage 2013, Oman forthcoming).

We Map Lights and Meteors: Configuring Citizen Science Participation In A Collaborative App Design Process *Nona Schulte-Römer, Helmholtz Centre Potsdam - GFZ German Research Centre for Geosciences; Friederike Klan, Deutsches Zentrum für Luft und Raumfahrt; Helga Kuechly, GeoForschungsZentrum Potsdam; Christopher Kyba, GeoForschungsZentrum Potsdam*

In our citizen science project *Nachtlicht BÜHNe* we are currently developing two mobile web applications in a participatory design process, in order to map light emissions (nightlight app) and fireballs (meteor app). Both apps are collaboratively designed by citizens and scientists for citizens and scientists, including ourselves. In the process, we are not only developing the apps, but also methods and means to facilitate reflexive prototyping and a participatory design process. In this paper, we reflect on these methods. First, we explore our "infrastructuring" work (Dantec and DiSalvo 2013) in various project stages. Second, we ask how our design choices configure and "inscribe the citizen scientist" (Woolgar 1991, Akrich and Latour 1992) in the apps we create. This applies to the citizen app co-developers, as we are constantly testing the app prototypes in their various development stages, and to future citizen app users that we are hoping to engage and inspire once the apps are ready for use. Third, we reflect on how we negotiated and navigated between app usability and data quality by developing 'just good enough interfaces' for collecting data for our multiple scientific, societal and political needs (cf. Gabrys and Pritchard 2018). Our methodological reflection profits from the fact that we can compare and contrast our different approaches and requirements in the participatory design of our two apps. We conclude with an outlook on what kind of world we hope to create with our project and approach.

Session Organizer:

Michiel Van Oudheusden, University of Cambridge

010. New Wars on Science I - Vaccines

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Participants:

Credibility and the ontologies of vaccine criticism : vaccine criticism in France from the H1N1 flu to COVID-19 *Jeremy Keith ward, Inserm*

Vaccine criticism is widely presented as a symbol of the contemporary « wars on science » and the growth of « anti-science movements ». In this presentation, I will show how this bears on credibility-building practices of French vaccine-critical activists and organisations. The presentation will draw on a variety of datasets : a qualitative and quantitative analysis of a sample of 254 French-speaking vaccine-critical websites, interviews with 30 of the main actors of vaccine criticism in France and an analysis of vaccine critics' appearances and mentions in the French press and television. I will show that a) these actors' criticism of vaccines reflect medical ontologies of varying degrees of heterodoxy, b) these medical ontologies are inseparable from political ontologies (also of varying degrees of heterodoxy), and c) that the less radical actors perform credibility by demarcating themselves from the more traditional forms of vaccine criticism (boundary-work). This leads to a fragmentation of the vaccine-critical milieu where only the less radical actors benefit from visibility in the mainstream media. I will conclude by discussing whether and how vaccine hesitancy in France can be interpreted as mistrust of science.

Science is too serious a business to be left to scientists *Paul Guille Escuret, CERMES3 - GEMASS - VITROME*

During the past few decades, vaccine controversies have multiplied and attracted more and more attention. But, while antivaccine movements and vaccine hesitancy have been extensively investigated, vaccine advocacy remains almost uncharted. This is particularly unfortunate as vaccination has almost become a compulsory topic when it comes to promote science, reason or progress. Moreover, whether it is to celebrate these values or to condemn their putative enemies, new forms of mobilisations have emerged and they involve new actors and new arenas. In this paper I propose to explore this blind spot by analysing french speaking « pro-vaccine » activism on the web. Both qualitative (interviews, netnography) and quantitative methods (large twitter database covering a three years period) have been mobilized with a special attention drawn to professions and rhetorics. This focus aims to examine the question through two different literatures. First, as critic movements are extensively studied, and as vaccine advocacy is predominantly built as a counter-movement, symetries can be questioned and nuances can be reinvested. Notably, it offers insight on the various ways in which actors seize vaccines, and on the consequences it has on their position within networks. Finally, I suggest to project the concept of boundary work on a borderline case : the new political sociology of science already developed what happens when science boundaries are framed by scientists with non-scientific incentives, but what happens when science boundaries are framed by non-scientists ?

The anti-vaccination movement and quantification: counting the dead to persuade the living *Sorina Vasile, University of Bucharest; Ana Cosima Rughinis, University of Bucharest*

The coronavirus pandemic and the vaccine information campaigns have drawn attention to the importance of communication using numbers - statistics, percentages, and data visualization. Quantification, as the production and communication of numbers (Espeland & Stevens, 2008) is an essential process of the contemporary scientific process, playing a role in redressing uncertainties, establishing trust, and exerting control (Mennicken & Espeland, 2019). The anti-vaccination movement also expanded in the new territory of Covid-19 vaccines and gained new arguments to justify vaccine hesitancy or refusal. Building on shared information resources with the biomedical infrastructure of knowledge, the anti-vaccination actors use different framings and interpretation of numbers to commensurate events (Espeland & Stevens, 1998) and amplify vaccination risks (Kasperson et al, 1987). In this paper, we use two case studies of media reports covering the deaths of two health workers following their Covid-19 vaccine. One event happened in Romania, and the other in the United States of America. Both deaths set in motion two similar lines of investigations that looked for and counted other similar adverse effects: one performed by the authorities and another one by the anti-vaccination groups. Using partly shared, partly diverging numbers, the two categories of actors came back with diametrically opposed conclusions in assessing one's risk of dying from the Covid-19 shot. We propose a conceptual framework in analyzing commensuration and quantification in both pro-vaccination and anti-vaccination groups, pointing towards the divergent methods in which actors produce, frame and interpret numbers in order to create relations between different entities to justify their worldviews.

Session Organizers:

Henri Boullier, French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)

Baptiste Kotras, INRAE, LISIS

011. Environ|Mental Urbanities: Problematizing 'the Mental' and 'the Urban' in Ethnographic Inquiry – I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

In ethnographic inquiries of urban atmospheres, biosocial relations and

bodies as practiced, social science scholars situate subjective, embodied experiences in between organisms and environments (Mol 2002, Blackman 2008, Ingold/Palsson 2013, Blok/Fariás 2016, Meloni et al. 2018; Seeberg et al. 2020). In doing so, they emphasize how bodily processes are permeated by environmental conditions. However, the adequacy of these approaches for the concomitant embodiment and ecological relationality of 'mental' experiences has hardly been addressed directly (among the exceptions are Fitzgerald et al. 2016 and Winz 2018). Relatively few ethnographic research projects attend to the mutual constitution of 'the mental' and 'the environmental' (Amin/Richaud 2020; Bister et al. 2016). In this panel, we seek to fill this research gap through empirically grounded ethnographic inquiries into 'mental phenomena' as part of 'urban' life. Our discussion embraces the following conceptual and methodological challenges: How can we grasp elusive aspects of experiences in and of the city as dynamic co-constitutive relations between material environments, cultural practices, subjective experiences, and urban infrastructures? What concepts, methods, and research designs are suitable for combining experience-based approaches (Söderström et al. 2016) with an inquiry in ecologies of expertise (Beck 2015) that shape the urban fabric? What is left of 'the mental' if we problematize it 'environmentally'? How does our research affect how we conceptualize 'the urban'? Finally, how could our studies inform the design of cities and the crafting of urban cohabitation (Bates et al. 2017)?

Participants:

Contracting Taskscapes: The Dissolution of Urban Mental Health Networks and the Effects on Clinical Response-ability *Lauren Cubellis, Freie Universität Berlin*

The transformation of urban environments alters the landscape of mental life; not just for service users and recipients, but for clinicians working to provide care under increasingly precarious conditions. Based on long-term ethnographic fieldwork with a community-based crisis intervention team in Berlin, this paper explores how financial trouble forced the spatial and temporal contraction of previously city-wide teams, undermining the capacity to maintain dialogically-attuned psychotherapeutic taskscapes (Ingold 1993). The reduced ability to make home visits, the negotiation of fewer working hours, the doubling up of teams in disappearing office space, and the loss of a city-wide network of services all forced practitioners to reconfigure how they interacted with service users and each other. Resentments, disagreements, feelings of clinical futility and frustration (Brodwin 2013) became anxious expressions of the real concern that they would be unable to provide the persistent attachment and attention that their understanding of "good care" demanded (Mol 2008). Under the weight of these changes, the care these clinicians valued in practice (Heuts & Mol 2007) became compressed; the aftershocks of contraction limiting their possibilities to sustain relationships with their clients and each other in response-able ways (Haraway 2008). In this case, taking stock of the conditions that shape environ|mental urbanities demands an attention not only to those on the receiving end of care services, but to the shifting taskscapes in which clinicians are working to provide them.

Un/Doing 'Home': Entanglements of the Mental and the Urban in Psychiatric Practices *Milena Bister*

In the history of asylum psychiatry, the relationship between the institution and the home carries a variety of meanings. For example, home, as well as a lack of home, could be the relations that brought someone into the asylum, but also the environment where protection from medical access was provided. The relationship of psychiatric asylums to large cities plays an equally important role in this history. Asylums were preferably built in rural areas remote from cities. Isolation and abuse of the mentally ill were a major criticism of the psychiatric reforms in the second half of the 20th century. The declared aim of the reform movements in many European countries was to establish community mental healthcare facilities, which would enable people to receive treatment in their familiar (urban) surroundings.

In this paper I deal with the entanglement of 'psyche' and 'city' at the beginning of the 21st century (cf. Söderström et al. 2016, Fitzgerald et al. 2016, Bister et al. 2016, Amin/Richaud 2020). The paper is based on an ethnographic analysis of the implementation of psychiatric home treatment in two public district hospitals in Berlin in 2016-17. In Germany, the English term "home treatment" is used for the treatment of people with acute psychiatric illness that is provided in their homes instead of hospital wards. The method is understood as a further step in deinstitutionalising psychiatry. The aim of the paper is to discuss in which ways 'home' emerges as a set of practices through which environments, mentalities, expertise and urbanities are enmeshed and coproduced.

Ecosocial modalities of care: Thinking change, in changing terms
Doerte Bemme, King's College London

The key innovation of an ecosocial perspective on mental life and distress is its emphasis on constant change: It allows us to conceptualize the mutual co-constitution of people and their habitats as a perpetually unfolding across time and space. An empirical focus on "niching" (Bister, Klausner, Niewöhner 2016) then asks us to conceive of mental life and distress as fundamentally in flux – as emergent, transient, rupturing, and characterized by feedback loops and unevenly accessible affordances. In this presentation, I explore what this might mean for practices of care and intervention. What are the evolving sites of such intervention? How can changing agencies and affordances be directed? I will draw on ethnographic examples of iterative intervention designs in Global Mental Health and of digital methodologies that passively collect "real time" data on everyday life to improve adolescent maternal mental health in rural Nepal. Through these examples, I ask: How are the good life accounted for in changing terms and parameters? And how can we imagine ecosocial modalities of care that are responsive to perpetually changing lifeworlds?

'Tidying up' and 'spilling out': Co-producing boundaries of place and need in community-based mental health services
Natassia Brenman, The University of Cambridge

The mental and the environmental are mutually implicated in the problem of access to mental healthcare. Shifting the dominant focus on 'hard to reach' communities, I am interested in the socio-material arrangements of access within spaces of inner-city mental health care: how does the making of place relate to the making of mental health need within such arrangements? This paper will revolve around the sociomaterial practices of 'tidying up' and 'spilling out' when it comes to managing the spatial boundaries of mental healthcare, as well as what constitutes 'appropriate need' in community-based services. I draw on ethnographic material from three such psychotherapy services in London, which all seek to include the excluded in UK mental healthcare. An ethnographic orientation towards practices at the 'doors' of each service provides mode of engaging with ways spatial boundaries and diagnostic boundaries in mental health care emerge co-constituent. For example, the way 'open door policies', as well as the dynamics of urban infrastructure at one site created anxieties about becoming a "dumping ground," and preoccupations with waste and "people out of place". This emerged in relation to the way in which eligibility criteria for these extra state services was all about "spilling out of the box" of diagnostic categories; a way in to care for those who may be "hard to place" in mainstream services. This pushes us to consider mental health need, not only as product of individual experience, but co-produced with places of inclusion and exclusion in the city's infrastructures of care.

Session Organizers:

Milena Bister

Tomás Criado, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Chair:

Patrick Bieler, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

012. Domesticating Pandemic Troubles: Modelling Covid-19 in an Uncertain World I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Modelling, a scientific practice once reserved for mathematicians, epidemiologists, ecologists and economists, has assumed sudden authority in the covid-19 pandemic. The commanding presence of models in global policy has prompted questions about evidence, reliability and trust. Predictions and forecasting, grounded in formalised assumptions, have shifted the landscape of acceptable evidence in global public health. Moreover, modelling became popular: scores of armchair epidemiologists shared their newfound wisdom, the R-number and "exponential growth" became household terminology, while hashtags like #flattenthecurve entangled "science into social practices, calculations into materialisations, abstracts into affects." (Rhodes et al 2020) In this panel, we will survey how pandemic modelling made relations since early 2020. We will reflect on the unprecedented ways in which pandemic modelling engaged with unequal and uncertain worlds. We encourage two kinds of contributions: 1) papers which consider the impact of pandemic modelling on knowledge production, policymaking and social relations in pandemic times. Such papers might ask what models do and how they perform as evidence and how modelling has shifted, accelerated or reconfigured persisting challenges of inequality, racism and colonialism. Authors might pay attention to local, regional or national frames of reference. 2) Papers, which investigate the making of relations within models and scrutinize how practices of modelling enfold social, geographical, ecological and microbiological assumptions when forecasting the pandemic world. We invite papers focusing particularly beyond Europe and North America to ask what constitutes good relations within modelling practices, and how we might reconcile these with an ethics of care, responsibility and solidarity.

Participants:

Ambiguous Futures: Thinking Through Uncertainty in Pandemic Modeling
Yui Fujii, University of Florida; Rebecca R Henderson, University of Florida; Marit Ostebo, University of Florida

COVID-19 models have, for the past year, overtaken the public imaginary. As politicians, scientists, organizations, and individuals have struggled for control in the midst of a sea of unknowns, predictive models have emerged as a prophetic device, granting an anxious public a glimpse into possible futures. Yet despite their seeming certainty, with some models predicting death and illness down to the level of the individual, a close examination of pandemic models reveal uneasy, shifting, and ambiguous futures, their very fabric interwoven with uncertainty and doubt. Drawing on qualitative interviews with pandemic modelers conducted before and during COVID-19, as well as public and scholarly modeling this paper seeks to understand the notions of uncertainty and risk that are embedded within predictive disease models. More specifically we investigate the sources of uncertainty within models of emerging epidemics, tracing the social and scientific forces and processes that shape their creation. We ask: What is uncertainty, how does it relate to the futures that are produced, and how does it figure into their creation? How do modelers navigate and address uncertainty in their publications and in communication with policymakers? How is uncertainty managed, controlled or uncontrolled? And how does uncertainty figure into notions of what models are, what they do, and how they may be used?

Domesticating modelling. A media analysis of modelling in the UK response to Covid-19
Lukas Engelmann, University of Edinburgh; Catherine Montgomery, University of Edinburgh; Steve Sturdy

Our paper traces the representation of pandemic modelling in UK print media from the emergence of Covid-19 to the implementation of the first UK-wide lockdown on March 23, 2020. Projections and inferences from Covid-19 modelling have shaped policy decisions and public responses to the pandemic in

unprecedented ways. We analyse how the UK print media has configured modelling as significant evidence tool in the representation of the pandemic. Interrogating generalised assumptions about the impact of modelling science, we argue that pandemic modelling has been configured differently at consecutive stages of the pandemic to explain, support or undermine covid-19 policy. We identify four different periods in the evolution of these intersecting frames. Initially, modellers, policy makers and media alike emphasised uncertainty surrounding available data, and hence the contingency of modelled projects, thus justifying a ‘wait and see’ approach to government intervention. With growing public pressure for government action, policy and media frames were adjusted to emphasise the importance of timing those interventions for best effect, with evidence from modelling mobilised to inform the temporal horizons. This gave way to a period of crisis, as the press increasingly questioned the reliability of the existing models and policies, and as modellers and policy makers dramatically revised their projections. Finally, with the imposition of the first UK lockdown, policy and media frames were brought back into alignment with one another, in a process of domestication through which the language of modelling became a basic resource for press discussion of the epidemic.

Global Common Sense: Crafting and Circulating the Pandemic in Models and Laws *Fleur Johns, UNSW Sydney*

Axiomatic, everywhere, to experiences of the COVID-19 pandemic are models. Struggles over the interlocking global crises that the pandemic has provoked—and what to do about them—translate, in many places, into struggles over the parsimonious representation of that which exceeds observation. Which, then, are the models wielding greatest authority in the COVID-19 pandemic? What claims and hierarchies are embedded in them? Where lie their centres and peripheries? With what or whom are they most concerned and to what or whom are they inattentive or indifferent? How do they relate, if at all, to the making and operation of laws? On the plane of the global, models have, at least since the interwar period, been as crucial to the assertion and mobilization of authority, and the crafting of global common sense, as treaties, social movements, and international institutions. To take account of the world-making and -remaking ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic, we must register and read closely how it is being modelled. This paper attempts such a close reading by devoting socio-legal attention to selected social distancing regulations around the world, and to the different kinds of models that inform and sustain their chains of reference. It aims to highlight what is at stake in the preference of one modelling technique over another, and in their combination with other local knowledges and laws, and to demonstrate, as a consequence, how vital is models’ iterative cross-referencing against other knowledge forms.

Taming and making viral trouble: Models and targets in the making absent and present of disease *Tim Rhodes, Centre for Social Research in Health, UNSW; Kari Lancaster, University of New South Wales, Sydney*

Enumerations govern. Modelled projections close down unknowns, and sources of dis-ease, thereby taming risk and affording security through calculus. Numerical targets, enabled by modelled projections, are key actors in policy assemblages of pandemic and epidemic control. In this paper, we explore how models and targets are put-to-use and made-to-matter inside policy assemblages of disease control. We draw on qualitative interviews with mathematical modellers, implementation scientists and policy experts, and other materials, to trace how models and modelled targets make-up as well as make absent-present disease. Our first case concerns the absenting of epidemic through the evidence-making of viral elimination future. Here, we focus on hepatitis C, and the performative potentials of models and targets inside global policy assemblages of viral elimination, in which the World Health Organization is a key

player. Our second case concerns the making present of viral threat through the evidence-making of pandemic as a means of risk governance. Here, we focus on COVID-19 and the life of models inside national policy assemblages of pandemic preparedness and response. Taken together, we trace how the virtual precision of models and targets affords a latitude in evidence-making to enable situated policy responses, where models are made-to-matter in multiple ways, both to enact viral presence as well as to make epidemics and their troubles disappear. We therefore explore the absence-presence of pandemic troubles as evidence-made in models, which of course are themselves not without trouble or controversy. Models then, become-with pandemic trouble.

Session Organizer:

Lukas Engelmann, University of Edinburgh

013. Evidence and perspectives of social innovation - I: Frameworks & Theoretical Approaches

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

In recent decades, several international organizations such as the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the European Commission and the World Economic Forum have stated that nation’s progress must be understood in a broader set of ideas, including not just technological innovation but also social innovation (SI). Although the term has been used in sociological discourses and within other disciplines since the late 19th century, SI has gained attention in academia and political discourses since the beginning of the 21st century. There are several conceptions about SI; the term is used differently across diverse disciplines. Conceptions go around “doing something good within or for society”, “changing social practices and/or structure”, or “contributing to rural and community development”. Likewise, there is an exponential growth of academic literature dealing with SI, so that an increase of success experiences is presumed. Like this, it is also presumed that SI is becoming the most convenient innovation paradigm to face the social, economic, political and environmental challenges of the 21st century. In response to this outlook, through this open panel we invited STS scholars to join a discussion on SI that presents empirical research results, showing evidence of specific SI processes, as well as perspectives that allow feedback on emerging practices, experiences and application. In the first session of the panel we will discuss different theoretical approaches dealing with different modes of social collaboration, new forms of social relations, social change and economical implications.

Participants:

Between conceptions and evidence of social innovation: a literature review *José Francisco Romero-Muñoz, Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla - Dirección de Innovación y Transferencia de Conocimiento; Wietse de Vries, Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla*

The term social innovation (SI) had been mentioned in academic literature since the late 19th century, yet it has gained real attention in academia (and political discourses) since the beginning of the 21st century. There is a growing literature on the subject, mostly from Anglo-Saxon countries and to a lesser extent from Spanish-speaking countries. Interest in social innovation continues to grow because it is usually presented as the most convenient innovation paradigm to face the social, economic, political and environmental challenges of the 21st century. The literature review that we present has aimed to explore and qualitatively describe empirical research trends on social innovation. To do this, we carried out a systematic search for arbitrated academic publications in the EBSCO database during the period from November 2019 to April 2020. We compiled 572 articles on the subject, published between 1971 and 2020. The main findings suggest that there are several conceptions about SI; the term is used differently between different disciplines. Various criticisms suggest that ambiguity persists in the term and that the existing body of literature is

incoherent. In addition, it is often mentioned that it is not clear whether it should be considered as a phenomenon or as a theoretical framework. However, most of the literature we analyzed presents cases of social innovation with different levels of success. The major contribution of this paper to the field of science and technology studies is the critical discussion about what would be the most appropriate way to evaluate cases of social innovation and the real lessons that they bring us.

Framing Circular Economy from a Social Innovation perspective *Isaac Ortega Alvarado, NTNU - Norwegian University of Technology and Science, Trondheim*

This paper aims to discuss how circular economy (CE) and social innovation (SI) can be complemented. I depart from the perspective of CE as a set of changes in the relation to how materials are approached and SI as changes in how social forms take place—one of which is the value given to objects as mediators of human relation. The concept of CE has been gaining relevance as one path to reach sustainability. While it has the favor of authorities at both private and public sectors at the local and international level, it is still a highly contested concept. The current academic discourse around CE grows in tension about the negotiating aspects of technical solutions and their implication for future societies. A fraction of the recent calls to implement and deepen on the matters of the CE set the focus on a need to include a social perspective to strengthen its impact on the common welfare. This is mainly recognized through cultural aspects of consumption that are at the base of unsustainability. In this paper, I explore the possibilities of underpinning circular economy as a set of social innovations (SI). This is done through a narrative analysis of current literature. I interpret technical infrastructures as shaping specific modes of relations which create a distinction to what is considered a CE in different parts of the world. These modes of relations in turn describe the kind of SI required to have a CE that is transformative at the structural level.

Social Innovations for Landing on Earth. *Gerald Beck, Hochschule München; Diego Compagna, Hochschule München*

In our paper, we develop an STS based analytical framework for evaluating social innovation for their suitability for “landing on earth” (Latour & Weibel, Critical Zones, 2020). The word “social” in social innovation can be confusing in at least two ways. First, some SI scholars make efforts to separate social innovation from technical innovation – an effort that seems obviously wrong from an STS perspective. Second, in some SI definitions “social” means an improvement for the greater good, while others deny a normative stance. However, among practitioners the necessity of a normative compass for social innovation is undisputed. STS has a long tradition to reflect on human–nonhuman relations beyond the modern conception of colonizing nature – be it entanglements (Donna Haraway), mushrooms (Anna Tsing) or terrestrial (Bruno Latour). We combine these approaches that are based on the distinction between being modern and being terrestrial or entangled with normative concepts of good relations with nature like Buen Vivir, One Health, Eco-Social Transformation, Gaia - to name a few. We want to bind STS with SI insights as well as make the diverse and growing field of SI projects more accessible for STS perspectives. Our empirical foundation are current research projects on SI and teaching in the BA “Management of Social Innovation”. We offer a perspective on SI that grounds the distinction between SI that just repair the status quo to transformative SI that is capable of thinking beyond the barriers of modernity and thus seek for a place to “land on earth”.

What is meant by social value? A systematic literature review *Lauren Withycombe Keeler, School for Future of Innovation in Society, Arizona State University; Luke Boyle, Arizona State University; Michael Bernstein, Arizona State*

University

Calls for innovation and innovation systems that create social value are growing. There is widespread recognition that not only does economic value fail to adequately account for the impact of business and innovation on society, but that failure has undermined public trust in businesses, governments, science, and financial institutions. A number of tools have been developed to consider social value alongside economic value, including Social Return on Investment (SROI) and Triple Bottom Line accounting. However, little attention has been paid to what is actually meant by social value. What are the benefits sought by a more comprehensive accounting of activities of corporations and systems of innovations? SROI considers social value to be, in part, providing money to a government in the form of taxes. But in the United States 54 cents of every tax dollar is spent on the military, and military spending is not widely regarded as having a net-positive social impact. Triple Bottom Line accounting often relies on harm reduction like ensuring that nowhere in the supply chain uses child or forced labor. But, not using slave labor is more of a minimum operational requirement than an aspirational goal capable of changing how public and private sector innovation happens and with what outputs and impacts. To understand what is meant by social value we present a systematic review of social value from 285 peer-reviewed articles: tracing the varied origins of the term, documenting its applications in distinct fields, identifying themes in how social value is understood, and analyzing how it is measured. We conclude with a definition of social value rooted in human need satisfaction and propose means of operationalizing this definition to drive innovation of social value as well as account for its impact.

Session Organizer:

José Francisco Romero-Muñoz, Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla - Dirección de Innovación y Transferencia de Conocimiento

014. Equality By Design Vs Design For Appropriation In Digital Resource Sharing - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Several scholars in STS (in platform and infrastructure studies, Plantin et al. 2018; see also in Internet studies, Dulong de Rosnay and Musiani 2020) have pointed to architectural features of profit-driven global digital infrastructures, e.g., GAFAM, that lead to concentrations of power, discrimination and inequalities. Conversely, egalitarian applications such as on-line peer-to-peer production platforms tend to fail the test of scaling up small communities of participants to egalitarian dynamics in large groups, thus sometimes falling back into profit-driven, hierarchical, and discriminatory modes of operation (Tréguer et al. 2020). The panel proposes to consider the problem of (in-)equalities and discrimination in information- (and possibly other resource-) sharing systems not as a consequence of system structure nor platform usage; rather, we encourage taking the opposite perspective: can inequalities be avoided from the outset. How can discrimination be hindered by the design of adequate architecture mechanisms for equality? What is the role of STS scholars in engaging with the design phase of systems? The panel invites empirical contributions where equality is considered, negotiated, contested in a system's architecture as an initial design value. The user communities of these systems need not to be large, nor their mode of function to be peer-to-peer. Contributions are invited to describe how the value of equality was designed in these projects and how it was to be integrated in, promoted by, or supported by the system's architecture.

Participants:

Eliminating the Cut Down from Science for Equality: Policies for Fair HPC Resource Utilization *Gökçe Nuhoğlu, Middle East Technical University; Arsev Umur Aydinoglu, Middle East Technical University*

Big data researchers depend on sophisticated infrastructures due to high computational needs. High Performance Computing

(HPC) infrastructures are established as centers to meet this demand. Researchers' equal access to these centers is one of the main problems. In the literature, there are some examples of democratization of the HPC resources. However, issues remain regarding the fair scientific utilization of HPC resources. In this study, we investigate the experiences of researchers affiliated with Turkish universities and using HPC centers regarding equality in access. We generate data through semi-structured interviews that are conducted with researchers in Turkey using HPC. The findings of the study show that centers in Turkey do not have a merit system for applications. Every researcher can benefit from the centers equally, but researchers have to endure long queue times due to the crowd. Researchers in provincial universities with limited budgets use central HPC resources with long queue times whereas researchers with budget opportunities tend to establish their own small local centers. These local computing centers used for small-scale research of a small coterie cannot meet the computing needs in large-scale research like national centers. Therefore, we recommend common infrastructure policies respecting fair benefit from resources. This study provides efficient HPC infrastructure utilization design policies to eliminate the discrimination of researchers.

Digital Academic Objects: A History of the Digital Object Identifier (DOI) and a Trajectory Towards Academic Algorithmic Governance *Leslie Chan, University of Toronto Scarborough; Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine*

In this paper we trace the history behind a key node in the digital infrastructure for academic publishing and research object management, the Digital Object Identifier (DOI), commonly referenced as providing a key service for academics--a stable and persistent identifier for ensuring the permanence of scholarship. Over the last twenty years, there has been a strong push by the DOI Foundation for the DOI to serve as the de facto standard for digital scholarly objects. This has led to growing network effects, creating lock-in for researchers and new forms of exclusion. We draw on a rich literature looking at governance by standards (DeNardis 2011; Gibbon & Henriksen 2012; Russell 2014); digital discrimination and algorithmic technologies (Apprigh et al. 2019; Eubanks 2018; Noble 2018); critiques of the neoliberal university (Fitzpatrick 2019; Karaganis 2018); and digital surveillance and identification technologies (Agre 1994; Browne 2015) to argue that beyond an identification standard, the DOI has served to transform scholarship into material for an extractivist surveillance economy. This transformation now allows publishers to track, monitor, and extract further profit from scholarly outputs. Those of us working in institutions of higher education are increasingly entangled in these new forms of algorithmic governance, which have become embedded in the very socio-technical infrastructures of scholarly knowledge production. We point to possibilities of community-designed and governed infrastructures and tools that could allow us to reclaim a knowledge commons as envisioned since the dawn of the web. Works Cited Agre, Philip E. 1994. "Surveillance and Capture: Two Models of Privacy." *The Information Society* 10 (2): 101–27. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01972243.1994.9960162>. Apprigh, Clemens, Wendy Hui Kyong Chun, Florian Cramer, and Hito Steyerl, eds. 2018. *Pattern Discrimination. In Search of Media*. Minneapolis: University of Minnesota Press. Browne, Simone. 2015. *Dark Matters: On the Surveillance of Blackness*. Durham: Duke University Press. DeNardis, L. (Ed.). 2011. *Opening Standards: The Global Politics of Interoperability*. MIT Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctt5hhmxcx> Eubanks, Virginia. 2018. *Automating Inequality: How High-Tech Tools Profile, Police, and Punish the Poor*. First Edition. New York, NY: St. Martin's Press. Fitzpatrick, Kathleen. 2019. *Generous Thinking: The University and the Public Good*. Baltimore: Johns Hopkins University Press. Gibbon, P., & Henriksen, L. F. 2012. A Standard Fit for Neoliberalism. *Comparative Studies in Society*

and History, 54(2), 275–307.

<https://doi.org/10.1017/S0010417512000047> Karaganis, Joe, ed. 2018. *Shadow Libraries: Access to Knowledge in Global Higher Education*. Cambridge, MA : Ottawa, ON: The MIT Press ; International Development Research Centre. Noble, Safiya Umoja. 2018. *Algorithms of Oppression: How Search Engines Reinforce Racism*. New York: New York University Press. Russell, A. L. 2014. *Open Standards and the Digital Age: History, Ideology, and Networks*. Cambridge University Press.

Trust, Blockchain-based Technologies, the Public Sector, and the Social Good *Balazs Bodo, University of Amsterdam, Institute for Information Law; Heleen Janssen, University of Amsterdam*

Decentralized technologies, self-sovereign identity systems, distributed ledgers, and other blockchain based systems are "trust-minimizing" technical infrastructures. Their trustworthiness is based on some technical and design properties, such as decentralization, and strong cryptography, rather than them being regulated, having impeccable governance, or being fully transparent, or accountable. Public institutions generally enjoy high levels of trust, and even if they are not trusted, they are embedded in complex frameworks that ensure their trustworthiness: they are subject to laws, public scrutiny, their decisions can be challenged, etc. The deployment of trust-minimizing technologies in high-trust / high-trustworthiness contexts may contribute to more trustworthy public services, but also threatens to replace such high-trust environments with a trust-minimizing technology of unknown trustworthiness. This contribution focuses on the following questions: How can high-trust public institutions implement trust-minimizing infrastructures? In case of low-trust institutions, what is the preferable way forward: replacing distrusted public entities with trust-minimizing technologies, or improving their trustworthiness? Should we implement a trust-minimizing architecture, or a trust-maximizing one?

Session Organizers:

Alain Sandoz, IIUN

Léa Maria Stiefel, Unil

Discussants:

Alain Sandoz, IIUN

Léa Maria Stiefel, Unil

015. How to Read the How-to, Part I: Rethinking the Tacit

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 *Virtual: 20*

Salomé Skvirsky (2020) defines the process genre, or "how-to"-ness, as "the sequentially ordered representations of making or doing something." Moving beyond the question of replicability in experimentation (e.g., Collins 1985), we take inspiration from Skvirsky to invite submissions that explore aesthetic qualities of the how-to genre in knowledge-making practices. Specifically, we want to extend her analysis to scientific and social-scientific manuals. In thinking about objects like field guides, ethnographic textbooks, ecological surveys, personal research journals, archeological codes and conventions, we ask: what kind of affects, attachments and aesthetic experiences are produced and reproduced in the doing of science and through its representation in manuals? Skvirsky focuses on absorption, but we also invite papers that explore other feelings like boredom, love, anxiety, resentment, awe, etc. How are they enabled by the "how-to" genre of the manual? And how does this genre produce, reproduce, and disrupt relations, good or otherwise, between knowledge producers, objects of study, disciplines, institutions, and places? The manual is also a genre of theory seen in the exemplar of J. L. Austin's *How to do Things With Words*, Bruno Latour's *Science in Action: How to Follow Scientists and Engineers through Society* and, to a certain extent, in Kate Brown's *Manual for Survival*. We therefore invite submissions that interrogate a "how-to" manual as an object of analysis, but also as a mode of STS analysis and theorization, or, better yet, written in the how-to genre itself!

Participants:

How To ... Make Clinical Sense *Anna Harris, Maastricht University*

The study of hand drawn illustrations in medical and scientific instruction has a long history in STS and the History of Science. In this paper, in which I will focus on instructions for novice doctors learning to make clinical sense (as part of a larger group project by the same name), I want to bring this existing work on the history of instructional illustration in conversation with several new elements. First, I weave in ethnographic findings from a ethnographic study of medical learning in the Netherlands, focusing on how drawn illustrations are used in practice, by learners and educators. Second, I look at what we might learn from juxtaposition of these illustrations with others in modular furniture assembling guides, recipes, birdwatching manuals and knitting patterns. I suggest that such illustrations speak to tensions in the need to localise and generalise, and allow for variation, abstraction and improvisation. Finally, I examine what can be learned from making instructions ourselves, as STS scholars, whether as hand-drawn illustrations, or videos, material artifacts or other forms. The feeling I would like to explore here is : playfulness. Through playful encounters with instructions I consider how such making can further our understanding of the role instructional materials (and those who make them) has in medical and other knowledge reproduction, particularly in regards to training perception and sensory orientation. There will be a take-home craft lesson involved in this last part, so participants can continue to experiment with following, and making their own instructions!

Kitchen Cognition: Crafting Experiments for Opening Science *Sarah Klein, University of Waterloo*

Methods reform movements in psychology and cognitive science have responded to the 'reproducibility crisis' by advocating top-down reforms to incentivize transparency, encourage replication, and discourage questionable research practices, often taking the form of Open Science and the preregistration of hypotheses. These reforms aim to improve the credibility of research by reconfiguring the relationship of scientific inscriptions, (including research plans, data, and publications) and research action. Amid debates around these methods reforms, this project reframes the "plans and situated actions" (Suchman 2007) of research. This paper shares preliminary analyses from a project called Kitchen Cognition. Kitchen Cognition stages a playful counterpoint to topdown methods reforms, aiming to open experiments up in their richness as epistemic and material performances. Structured around a simple performance score, it asks a set of cognition researchers, at home in their kitchens, to design an experiment using what they have available. Employing remote video ethnography, I invite scientists into a collaborative feedback process of screening, transcribing and analyzing their responses to the prompt. By staging experimental design in the domestic space of cooking and recipes, this project highlights material, situated, and embodied features of experiments which are relegated to the background in abstracted and proceduralized accounts configured by mainstream methods reforms. In staging the 'plans' of experimental designs as 'situated actions', this project engages in collaborative 'making and doing' with scientists, contributing to discussions in STS about the function of instructions, science as craft, and efforts to open science's epistemic and methodological diversity.

Tips in Science: Notes from Ugandan Molecular Biology *Sandra Calkins, Free University of Berlin*

Molecular biology as a scientific practice depends upon research protocols that outline a sequence of steps to be taken and standardize the production of experimental evidence. This depiction could have come straight out of a molecular biology textbook. Based on fieldwork in a Ugandan molecular biology lab, this paper examines an additional informal and non-codified

layer of everyday labor and practice that even STS has rarely addressed—namely, the passing on of tips. Tips are not part of a formalized body of knowledge that is written down and archived, like the experimental protocols, but rather they are often passed on through oral explanation and suggestion, gestures, and ad hoc demonstration. In the Ugandan lab where I worked, although tips were deemed inessential to testing procedures, they were still daily exchanged and passed on in informal learning sessions and played a role in making repetitive lab routines easier and more efficient. I relate the dismissal of tips from the standard accounts of science to their reliance on a type of knowledge and feeling of the hand, skilled ways of haptically manipulating mundane research materials that cannot be fully expressed in words.

Typography of a Nation: How to Craft Digital Typefaces in Post-Crash Thailand *Boyd Ruamcharoen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)*

After the 1997 financial crisis, Thailand witnessed an efflorescence of cultural forms that sought to re-territorialize "Thainess." In this presentation, I consider "craft typography" as one such cultural form. Coming into vogue in this period, the personal computer remained alien and alienating to the Thai user, thanks to not only its foreign provenance, but also poor and limited support for the Thai language. How did Thai typeface designers, then, wrestle with the task of representing the "autochthonous" Thai identity in a "foreign" technological medium like the computer? To answer this question, I offer a cultural analysis of two texts: first, a how-to guide for beginners in typography by Roj Siamruay, a respected designer with a conservative tilt; and second, an anonymous online polemic that likened typography to utilities—specifically, tap water—in order to disabuse of a prominent politician's public claim that typefaces were not subject to copyright law, because the Thai language belonged to the nation as a whole. By teasing out the orientation to the process of cultural production that these two texts championed, I argue that Thai typographers reconciled the autochthonous "content" (Thai national language) and the foreign technological "medium" (the computer) by treating typography as a craft both in rhetoric and in practice, allowing them to downplay their alienation from their means of cultural production. If the how-to form, here, emphasized the importance of tacit knowledge as STS scholarship often does, it did so only to fold it into the project of nationalism.

Session Organizer:

Boyd Ruamcharoen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Chair:

Emma Pask, University of Chicago

016. Mediation, Probability, and Environmental Risk - I: Chance and Temporalities of Environmental Risk in the Anthropocene

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

In recent years, the looming prospect of extinction, climate crisis, and global environmental degradation has often been met with narratives of eco-apocalypse or eschatology. Yet, invocations of existential risk are also frequently co-opted for the purposes of technocratic solutionism, which often constrains imaginaries around environmental futures and privileges existing modes of instrumentalist thought. This session reflects on these contemporary orientations towards climate crisis, describing and analyzing the temporal politics around an increasingly urgent and catastrophic imaginary of the Anthropocene. Beginning with a critique and articulation of the tech sector's orientation towards existential risk, these contributions explore alternative, affirmative, and emergent discourses around the Anthropocene. This includes a discussion of the politics of delay and suspension around cryopreservation as a response to perceived existential risk that works by extending the present rather than managing uncertainty, as well as the role of reflexivity in infrastructural management and repair. Mobilizing an STS perspective, participants examine discourses in

science, technology, and popular media to consider how technological developments converge with social and cultural mediations risk.

Participants:

Three Critiques of Existential Risk *Derek Woods, Rice University; Joshua Schuster, Western University*

Emerging from analytic philosophy, especially the work of Nick Bostrom, the study of “existential risk” is the study of any risk that might lead to absolute human extinction, from extreme global warming to nuclear winter to malevolent AI. The goal of existential risk analysts is ambitious: to establish IPCC-like institutions to study and mitigate the probabilities of risks that can only happen once, so that, having no precedent, we will only know that they are possible when it is too late. Accordingly, for proponents such as Sir Martin Rees, these risk analysts will have earned their funding if the science-fiction-like scenarios they project fail to materialize. In recent years, existential risk has become increasingly popular. The field boasts Ted Talks with millions of views, attracts funding from tech billionaires such as Elon Musk, and features in articles published by *The Economist*, *The New Yorker*, *Wired*, and other high-profile venues. With my co-author Joshua Schuster, I have been studying this field in its cultural contexts. Because of its many philosophical and political blind spots, we question it in a short book entitled *Three Critiques of Existential Risk*. But our largely negative critiques do move in two affirmative directions: 1) existential risk can be a backdoor for understanding the role of science fiction in powerful Silicon Valley worldviews; 2) the critique of existential risk is a compelling interface between the specialist humanities and popular culture, one at which to think the place of apocalypse and eschatology in contemporary media.

“The Great Dithering”: Cryopreservation, Climate Crisis and the Emergence of a Politics of Suspension *Thomas Lemke*

Donna Haraway has suggested the label “the Great Dithering” (2016: 144) to denounce the contemporary political and social situation of non-action in the light of the massive ecological crisis and climatic challenges. In my talk, I’d like to relate this observation to the emergence of cryobanks which deep-freeze organic material of endangered or extinct animal species, keeping them in a state of “suspended life” (Lemke 2019). These “frozen zoos” are considered the key to the protection of biodiversity in the light of climate crisis and the decline and extinction of whole species (Friese 2009, 2013; Chrulw 2011, 2017; van Dooren 2015, 2017). They are more than sites of conservation and storage, since they also provide the material resources for the potential resurrection of extinct species. Building on and extending Leon Wolff’s argument (2020) in his study of the Svalbard Global Seed Vault (SGSV), I argue that this “politics of suspension” in frozen zoos substantially differs from rationalities of prevention and preparedness. It does not react to a given uncertain future, seeking to adapt to or to accommodate it, but rather acts directly on temporal horizons by extending the present. The talk will examine the ambivalences of this “politics of suspension”. While it mobilizes suspended life to expand the duration of the present to keep options open, it might also delay essential changes or postpone decisions. The “cryopolitics” (Kowal and Radin 2015) of suspension risks contributing to tendencies to preserve the status quo by putting on hold necessary political and social transformations.

Infrastructural Globalism and the Ethics of Repair in the Anthropocene *Benjamin Hayden Sims, Los Alamos National Laboratory; Christopher R. Henke, Colgate University*

STS researchers increasingly recognize the crucial role of repair and maintenance in the life cycles of infrastructures and other technologies, a topic we explore in our book *Repairing Infrastructures: The Maintenance of Materiality and Power*. Like others studying these topics, we see repair and maintenance as under-recognized activities that can potentially play a key role in creating a more sustainable and equitable future. However, as

humanity moves deeper into the Anthropocene, we also move deeper into what Ulrich Beck and others have called reflexive modernity, a situation in which the risks and externalities of sociotechnical systems increasingly reverberate back on us in unexpected ways. This reflexivity has a strong infrastructural component, as infrastructure systems and governance have become increasingly globalized, and even our ability to understand the global impacts of human activity relies on massive information and data gathering infrastructures. Given these circumstances, repair and maintenance activities may also carry unexpected risks and externalities, and can play a role in perpetuating unsustainable infrastructures and unjust power structures. We propose that ethical repair and maintenance of infrastructures in the Anthropocene requires a reflexive perspective that takes into account the impacts of these activities across multiple scales and social groups. We close with some guidelines for practicing reflexive repair.

Session Organizer:

Lisa Han, Arizona State University

Discussant:

Yuriko Furuhashi, McGill University

017. Mapping the Conceptual Vocabulary of AI in the Global South - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

The possibilities of leveraging Big Data through AI-based interventions are often poised to flow as innovations emerging from the Global North as the active center to the Global South as the passive periphery. Problematizing these flows, this panel is oriented towards showcasing that the Global South is neither a passive recipient, nor is it the periphery of these innovations. The panel invites submissions that identify new and/or reinterpret old concepts and keywords that underlie the emerging meaning(s) and future(s) of AI in the Global South. The range of conversations on this topic operates on a wide spectrum between optimism of leapfrogging and digital transformation of societies on one end and the pessimism of human suffering caused by new forms of data capitalism and colonialism on the other. Mapping this spectrum, the members of this panel will not only present their concepts, keywords, research methods, and case studies in understanding the building and consequences of these technologies, but also collaboratively engage with each other in developing a broader conceptual vocabulary of AI in the Global South. The panel asks what stories of AI are told and shared, what unequal and uncertain world(s) do these stories build, what hopes and concerns do they amplify, and what future(s) do they imagine in the Global South. After all, the concepts and keywords to describe the mutual shaping of AI and society have different intellectual trajectories in different parts of the world. Recognizing this difference is the first step towards understanding it.

Participants:

From artificial subject to new alienation: debates of AI-human relations in contemporary China *Julie Yujie Chen, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto; Yuxing Zhang, University of Toronto*

The paper presents an exploration into the debates among Chinese scholars on artificial intelligence (AI) and its relationship with human from the late 1970s to the contemporary era. Tracing the genealogy of the debates in the Chinese literature, we examine how the development of the AI, evolving and situated philosophy of science and technology, and the socio-economic and cultural forces inside and outside China co-shape the imagination of AI and the narratives of human and AI in China. Since the late 1970s to early 1990s when the influence of Marxian tradition, particularly historical materialism and the dialects of nature, remained strong and the application of AI in China was limited to the expert system, the debates of AI concentrated on the epistemology and human/machine subject. While the debates on the expert system continued into the 1990s, the narratives of AI gradually shift to entangle the technology

with smart social governance and national development. China's position in the global knowledge production system and capitalism produces a profoundly contradictory narrative of AI-human relations in the new millennium—warning against “a new alienation” of human beings on one hand and a justification of exploiting reserve army of human labor for data-driven AI development on the other. The existing STS studies on AI and/in China tend to focus on policy analysis and critiques of the surveillance regime. The paper enriches the current knowledge by elucidating the interplay between technology, intellectual traditions, social, economic, and cultural factors in shaping the narratives of AI in China.

From Data As A Means Of Knowledge About Publics To "Data Publics" *Florence Millerand, Université du Québec a Montreal - UQAM; Alexandre Coutant, UQAM; Mélanie Millette, UQAM; Guillaume Latzko-Toth, Université Laval*

While data have the potential to empower social actors who have the means to make sense of them, little research explicitly addresses the publics involved in datafication processes: to what extent is the so-called wealth of data actually used, by which publics, how and for what purpose? How do the actual users and uses match or differ from the publics imagined and targeted by the instigators of data production and publication projects? Alongside the notions of "calculated publics" and "datafied publics", which emphasize the algorithmic objectification of publics through the data they generate, we propose the term "data publics" to designate social subjects who actively interact - or are supposed to interact - with the data made available to them. This paper will bring theoretical and empirical foundations to the concept of "data publics", which we propose as a heuristic for thinking about the sociopolitical aspects of datafication. Three case studies of organizations involved in the production and publication of public and private data will serve as an empirical basis for the presentation: a municipal open data portal, a platform for personal data related to health, a collective of data scientists working for community groups. The methodology consists of an ethnography of each organization, combined with document analysis and interviews.

Theorizing Dataisms embedded within a 'Toolkit': An Activist Perspective *Tuisha Sircar, Council for Social and Digital Development; Pranav Menon, Research Scholar, Centre for Study of Law and Governance, Jawaharlal Nehru University*

A toolkit in an online social movement is equivalent to a pamphlet or flier that is used on ground movements to mobilise and create awareness regarding a particular cause or protest. It provides for a set of guidelines coupled with information that establishes how a particular goal is to be achieved. Toolkits are typically made for social media campaigns, mass emailing authorities as well as includes details on promoting the campaign through different platforms. Several online platforms like Jhatkaa, Change.org, Let India Breathe, India Against Hate, etc., have made toolkits for protesting against unjust laws and policies of the government such as the Citizenship Amendment Act, Environmental Impact Assessment Notification, Network Neutrality policy or Transgender Bill. Recently, the movement against the three farm laws saw a lot of traction both through offline as well as online campaigns. A toolkit developed by Extinction Rebellion, a loose knit radical environmental action group India on how to engage in solidarity actions with the farmers as well as avenues to participate in the movement, caught the limelight due to Greta Thunberg's tweet. This led to spontaneous arrest of an activist Disha Ravi and threat of arrest for two other activists Nikita Jacob and Shantanu Muluk. This paper seeks to look at the emergence of the toolkit that created a nationwide storm in two ways. First we seek to understand how the toolkit functions as a *modus operandi* for activists. In this regard, we intend to locate the free flow of information that is provided as an ideal type in a society which is data-driven.

Second, we seek to understand how the toolkit functions as a pawn for the state to surveil the citizens against anti-state movements. In this regard, there is restriction on the dissemination of information. The movement is curtailed by the state as policies that restrict a data-driven society are put into place. The questions of data sovereignty competing with data justice comes into the fore as data politics engenders the entire discourse. Surveillance has become omnipresent in our contemporary society. Ranging from the state's surveillance architecture and the rise of corporate driven datafication that collects information indiscriminately to lateral surveillance by private citizens and mobs have embedded in our day to day lives in fundamental ways. More significantly, the rampant methods of surveillance and data collection have become integral to most forms of digital communication technologies we use in our day to day lives. Such modes of control raises the concern over grave violation of individual and collective privacy. So, what's left of a toolkit that from a tool for mobilization and collective organization for activists becomes a compromised set of datasets and algorithms to trample upon freedoms of citizens in the guise of national security? The Toolkit which ought to be envisioned as a beacon to facilitate data justice for activists becomes privy to sovereign diktats of the datafied state. This piece intends to tread around the debates between data justice and data sovereignty and provide a thick description of activist strategies to counter the tactics of datafication propagated by the state as well as market agents.

Artificial Intelligence Strategies in Latin America: Governing by Wording? *María Belén Albornoz, FLACSO Latin American Social Studies Faculty; Henry Chavez, CTS-Lab FLACSO / Divergence*

Since 2016, national artificial intelligence strategies have multiplied around the world, and in the past few years, the Latin American region has followed this emerging trend. This paper presents a comparative analysis of the conceptual vocabulary used in AI strategies and policies of Mexico, Chile, Argentina, Colombia, Uruguay and Ecuador. Based on this content analysis, we analyze several cases of artificial intelligence projects implemented in those countries to contrast the convergences and divergences in the discourse used by policy makers, practitioners and other stakeholders. Although data governance and artificial intelligence policies are standardizing a global language, we are interested in understanding how artificial intelligence concepts and imaginaries are depending on the types of actors involved, and the institutional culture of Latin American countries. The artificial intelligence strategies examined allowed us to inquire into how sociotechnical systems can operate in various cultural contexts in favor of State control, the market or citizens' rights. We are particularly interested in understanding what problems are being addressed by the use of artificial intelligence solutions and how these problems are framed in technological terms. In sum, technological design responds to belief systems that must be studied in order to understand how peripheral countries co-produce intellectual trajectories rather than being passive recipients of technological transfer.

Session Organizer:

Ranjit Pal Singh, Data & Society Research Institute

Chair:

Noopur Ravai

018. Markets as data - II - Datasets and the Platformization of the economy

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

STS scholars have long been interested in the diverse devices that equip markets, from market infrastructures to mundane marketing tools such as shopping carts, knowledge devices, and measuring instruments. As markets are digitized, consumer records, scoring and targeting instruments, trading

machines, and so on are key to how markets operate. Data act as a versatile, yet vital, apparatus for markets, playing crucial roles in the form of devices, valuation tools, infrastructures, and assets. This panel will explore these various facets of data, and how they help to bring markets into being. We welcome empirical and theoretical investigations of markets as data. First, with big data technologies, marketing knowledge is increasingly produced from the analysis of large databases that combine heterogeneous arrays of information on consumers, products, firms, and market operations. These data are then stabilized through metrics, dashboards and standards. How do these new “data objects” and knowledge devices reconfigure practices? Second, data streams are fueling automation or decision-making systems: matching algorithms, trade desks, recommendation engines, smart contracts, market screening mechanisms, dashboards. How does automation reconfigure firms’ practices in markets? Third, data are increasingly marketized themselves, harvested from public-facing services such as social media. How do markets for data impact “conventional” markets? Finally, data practices are increasingly subject to specific governance that is often the object of fierce contestation: from regulation such as GDPR in Europe, industry-level self-regulation and labelling processes, to local framing within firms. How does the governance of data, and its contestation shape markets and marketization practices?

Participants:

Governance challenges in the ‘Big Tech’ era: Will a reinvigorated competition policy solve the problems with personal data markets? *Kean Birch, York University; D.T. Cochrane, York University*

There is an emerging popular, policy, and political focus on competition law and policy as the solution to the governance challenges created by data markets increasingly monopolized by Big Tech. However, the emphasis on competition – as analytic, law, or policy – can only go so far in providing an answer to these challenges; these issues go beyond perceptions of data gathering as a violation of personal privacy or the monopolization of personal data as an effect of weak antitrust enforcement. Rather, our argument is that data markets are constituted by Big Tech’s wider ecosystems, which are governed through contractual arrangements and contract law. An ecosystem can be understood as a techno-economic assemblage of interconnected products, services, and platforms, as well as users, developers, and suppliers; crucially, it is the contractual arrangements that keep users and user data within an ecosystem as assets to be monetized. Our aim in this paper is to illustrate and analyse the relevance of contracts in the collection, use, and exploitation of personal data in digital ecosystems. As a result, we argue that personal data should not be seen as a ‘natural resource’ from which anyone can extract value; rather, data has to be made valuable through its conversion into a techno-economic object. And, here, the contract is an essential component of ecosystem monetization by Big Tech firms. Consequently, in order to address the governance challenges resulting from the dominance of Big Tech requires a rethinking of contract and contract law.

Sabotage, on-demand: On (un)profitability, power, and the platform asset *Aaron Shapiro, The University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill*

Why are so many “unicorns”—tech startups valued at over \$1 billion—so unprofitable? Put differently, why are unprofitable platforms so highly valued? Van Doorn and Badger (2020) theorize that financialized platform capitalism involves a process of “dual value production,” comprised, first, of the monetary value of the platform service (a taxi ride, a delivered meal, etc.), and second, of the speculative value attached to the data generated by the fulfilment of that service—what they call the data asset (see also Beauvisage & Mellet, 2020). My goal with this paper is to complement the assetization thesis by building on the Veblenian theory of “capital as power” (cf. Nitzan & Bichler, 2009). Specifically, I propose that the construction of the data asset’s speculative value depends on the platform’s capacity for

sabotage. Veblen understood sabotage as a “conscientious withdrawal of efficiency” and a primary means of inter-capitalist competition (Knoedler, 1992). Although platforms profess to increase efficiency (especially in the movement of goods and people on the “last mile” of supply chains), I aim to elaborate, first, the narrow definitions of “efficiency” by which they operate, and second, the techniques platforms use to sabotage multiple actors: (i) platform consumers, (ii) platform workers, (iii) competitors, and (iv) regulators. To the extent that these techniques utilize proprietary data culled from platform transactions, sabotage cannot be analytically separated from data-assetization. Moreover, the speculative ends through which data assets acquire value are themselves sabotage efforts. The paper invites further research into the dynamic relationship between data, assetization, and sabotage in and beyond platform economies.

Where does the value of data lie? Conflicting perspectives on the development of the data economy *Thomas Beauvisage, Orange Labs; Kevin Mellet, Sciences Po - CSO*

A ‘mainstream’ narrative about the data economy emerged some ten years ago, linked to the rollout of technologies and promises around big data. From an analogy with petroleum, data was presented as “new oil”, i.e. raw material that needs to be extracted, refined, put into circulation and utilised. From this perspective, data forms a still dormant new asset class that is just waiting to be converted into revenue streams. Expectations around these new assets have produced trillion-dollar projections (BCG 2012, Deloitte 2017). Drawing on an analysis of lay reports on the data economy and building upon a five years long empirical investigation into the field of ‘data marketing’, this paper investigates how the data economy is assessed and the different representations that support these assessments. Reports identify two distinct valuation processes: i) data as a tradable product (marketing segments, credit scores) exchangeable on the “data marketplace”; ii) data as a new asset class for companies, based on internal investments in information systems and organizational change. The first valuation process is paradoxically systematically put forward, and often confused with the ‘data economy’, even though it is economically less significant. By focusing on quantitative assessments, these reports tend to overlook another valuation mechanism, in the form of data infrastructures and standards for whole economic sectors, such as advertising, automotive or agriculture. This process is a way for tech companies to capture value in the long run, and to capitalize on new forms of digital rentiership.

Connecting Everything: Datafication, Rebranding and Regulation in the Emergence of a Smart City Market in Brazil *Jess Reia, McGill University; Luã Cruz, University of Campinas; Pedro Augusto Pereira Francisco, Igarapé Institute*

“Smart city” is one of those concepts that simultaneously embodies multiple meanings and engenders controversies. It often represents a corporate-driven narrative focused on achieving efficiencies through the use of data and real-time monitoring systems. City governments are implementing technologies framed in a specific narrative of “smartness” that continually fail to take into account questions of digital rights and data governance. We consider the smart city technopolitical agenda—as the incorporation of networks, data and infrastructure—the physical embodiment of an attractive market that not only responds to the pursuit of efficiency but also creates a consistent demand for smarter services and products. This paper offers a critical, Global South perspective on the emergence of the smart city market in Brazil, focused on power relations, rankings, corporate storytelling, data governance, and the rebranding process many companies go through to look smarter (from speed radars to smart sensors, for example). We assess the implications of regulatory frameworks and the role of

expos in shaping the market and selling an idea of selective connectedness. The research project was designed in 2017, and fieldwork was conducted between 2018 and 2020, with three cities serving as case studies: São Paulo, Curitiba, and Rio de Janeiro. We employ a regulatory framework and policy analysis as well as in-depth interviews with government representatives, companies, and researchers; participant observation in the largest smart city forums and expos in Brazil; and access to information requests.

Session Organizers:

Thomas Beauvisage, Orange Labs
Donald MacKenzie, University Of Edinburgh
Kevin Mellet, Sciences Po - CSO
Zsuzsanna Vargha, ESCP Business School

Chair:

Donald MacKenzie, University Of Edinburgh

019. Practicing Process Ontology in and with Biological Research – I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Biomedical fields increasingly understand life not as genetically determined, but as developing in relation to socio-material experiences. STS has discussed this development as the emergence of a postgenomic era or the biosocial turn, exploring how it changes views on genetics, bodies, their temporality and relationship to environments. For instance, engagements with environmental epigenetics, the microbiome, or viruses, reorient attention towards conceptualising phenomena, such as environment or disease, as relational entities across time and space. Thinking with relationality is an approach we can also find in the philosophy of biology. Dupré (2018, 2020) and others further the notion of process ontology; a theory, which understands biological phenomena as constantly stabilising processes with and in their environments instead of closed entities. While we can observe attempts of biologists themselves to address life as processual in research designs (e.g., applying a life-course perspective), we seek to make a shift in the ontological status of biological thinking more explicit: how does biology come from theory to practice and vice versa? This panel aims to further discussions on process ontology in STS and to consider how an interdisciplinary processual research agenda could look like in method and practice (Niewöhner/Lock 2018). We invite theoretical works that discuss how process ontology might inform biological theory as well as empirical engagements on how it becomes known experimentally and with what effects for understanding life. We also encourage ethnographic stories that make good relations visible (e.g., symbiotic relationships), contrasting prevailing reductionist accounts on health and disease in biology.

Participants:

Arrest, Reverse, Continue: Cryogenic Life between Object and Process
Veit Moritz Braun, Goethe University Frankfurt/Main

The emergence of cryotechnology (i.e. procedures involving the freezing of living matter for subsequent thawing) over the past century has given rise to the ability to stop life and make it resume. Stored at temperatures of down to -196°C , living tissue and cells can be turned into stable cryo-objects. Unlike genetic engineering or cell culture, however, cryotechnology is often presented as a neutral technology, conserving rather than transforming life. Drawing from A. N. Whitehead's process ontology and Isabelle Stengers's work on thermodynamics, I reflect on the prerequisites for such a technology to become truly "neutral" with respect to life. In the case of living matter, it implies that the transformation into a stable, frozen object can be fully reversed through thawing: nothing has happened after all, life goes on. This idealised conception of cryotechnology is complicated in two ways: by its relationship with other technologies of life that are often employed alongside it and by a notion of life that transcends the cell or the body as privileged sites of life. Discussing a series of failed attempts to revive

extinct animal species with the help of cryotechnologies since the early 2000, I argue that instead of stabilising life as an object we might as well understand these techniques as relaying life as a process - and thus productive rather than neutral.

Vaccines As Encounters
Roberta Pala, University of New South Wales, Sydney

In keeping with the theme of this conference and the current pandemic times, I would like to share my work on vaccines as encounters. Rather than considering vaccines as stable objects, whose complex workings provoke controversies that then become politicised, my work shows it is more productive to think of vaccines as a series of situated material encounters that are already pervasively political. By looking at specific empirical moments of vaccines' workings, I explore the challenges and complexities that animate scientific debates and practices around vaccines, I question and rethink the discourses that often fix these phenomena as something stable and neutral, and I claim that new ethical and political possibilities can emerge when we think of vaccines as multiple realities that come to exist through encounters. I look at the relations that vaccines produce with pathogens (via imitation), challenging ideas of nature and science; with the multispecies bodies that come together in the laboratory, showing vaccines' indebtedness to hierarchies of nonhuman bodies; with the immune system, focusing on the phenomenon of immunological memory that embodies specific understandings of time and predictions that are world-making and elusive; and with communities of bodies (through herd immunity), leaving open the possibility to think of bodily solidarity and collaborative understandings of being together. As Barad shows, political and ethical accountabilities are constantly produced and re-created through material relations, what she calls intra-actions, which means that thinking of vaccines as encounters can already be a transformative political practice.

Modeling Mothering: Process Ontology in/as Interdisciplinary Research Practice
Bican Polat, Tsinghua-Michigan Society of Fellows

Drawing on the work of Dupré (2012, 2015, 2020), this paper explores the historical development and current activity of three research groups that investigate social-emotional development in infancy as an eminently relational and constantly evolving life process. Examining this vital phenomenon within the context of the mother-infant relationship, these research groups have been studying its relational states from three different disciplinary perspectives – neurobiological, psychophysiological, and infant-observational. All three models construct early social-emotional development as an ensemble of dyadic regulatory processes and track its significant milestones in relation to both "social" and material environments. These models however differ in the way they conceptualize these biosocial entanglements and their psychopathological consequences. Each research team uses a different disciplinary matrix to break down the relational states of the mother-infant dyad to their measurable components. While the neurobiological and psychophysiological models reduce these dyadic states to bodily transactions within their respective target organisms, the infant-observational model characterizes them in terms of meaningful exchanges in a two-person social field. Consequently, while the former models explain pathogenesis in terms of neurophysiological dysregulation, the latter defines it in terms of failures in intersubjective communication. Using three models with interconnected concerns as a case study, I explore potentials of interdisciplinary collaboration and coordination across their respective disciplinary matrices. Combining historical research with ethnographic inquiry, I analyze the investigative practices and cognitive structures of these research groups and bring these analyses to bear upon the problem of building a pluralist, processual research agenda (Dupré 2015; Niewöhner & Lock 2018).

Bio-Psycho-Social Complexity and Epigenetics: Constructing

Biosocial Representations and Interventions *Luca Chiapperino, University of Lausanne*

This paper explores three strategies scientists adopt to cultivate the bio-psycho-social complexity of the epigenetic markers of psychiatric conditions. First, I illustrate the ontological work of tracing that lies behind the production of an epigenetic biomarker of traumatic experiences. These experimental practices provisionally connect experiences/exposures to biological functioning and rest upon a highly precarious choreography of elements from distinct ontological orders. Technical, epistemic and moral considerations have in fact to be carefully poised to produce the embodied traces of trauma in this type of laboratory research. Second, I single out how unstable knowledge of “epigenetic biomarkers” is made to hold through extrapolation of these biological traces across different animal models and human studies. The convergence of distant clues such as cross-species homologous processes requires a specific work – conditional to the erasure of suppositions, differences, gaps and uncertainties – prioritising consistent biological pathways across living beings. Extrapolation allows researchers to actively transform unfinished mechanistic knowledge in animal models into clinically relevant markers of bio-psycho-social complexity in humans. This stabilisation of translational knowledge requires, however, also the enrolment of biomedical actors closer to patients (e.g., clinicians, public health practitioners). This third strategy designates the need for a shared epistemic territory of confidence in this endeavour. Interdisciplinarity- and complexity-talks play here a crucial role not only to tame epistemic uncertainties, but also to produce a discursive inclusion of other contextual considerations (e.g., psycho-social determinants of health, living conditions, etc.) in the production of epigenetic aetiologies of disease.

Session Organizers:

Sophia Rossmann, MCTS, Technical University of Munich
Georgia Samaras, Munich Center for Technology in Society, Technical University of Munich

Chair:

Sophia Rossmann, MCTS, Technical University of Munich

020. Practices And Methods Towards Good Relations With Robots And AI I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Participants:

Building Good Relations With AI: Therapeutics, Mental Health, And Future Objects *Deborah Blizzard, Rochester Institute of Technology; Aya Jawad, Rochester Institute of Technology*

In her introduction to *Evocative Objects: Things We Think With*, Sherry Turkle reminds readers that “...acknowledgement of the power of objects has not come easy” for those who investigate the social and emotional meanings that the objects help to create (Turkle 2007:6). Over time, however, some scholars have started to think about things as important variables in the formation of human relationships. What makes these relationships “good relations” when both terms are contextually driven, and in the former case, morally defined? In this paper we take up the challenge to envision a future where a morally amorphous object, an erotic doll, might be useful in mental health practices. Currently, some therapeutics use forms of AI embodied in facsimiles of living things (e.g., PARO the robotic seal is used with some elderly patients when treating dementia). Objects like PARO draw from the familiarity of the object and the good relations that it invokes in patients. At the same time, companies building erotic companions (erotic dolls) are also finding ways to bring AI into the relationship with its owner. Considering both trajectories, this paper examines whether these forms of objects could merge into a new approach in medical therapy, particularly for the elderly. Drawing upon existing studies of robotic animal

therapy, we ask how these studies of objects and their already normalized processes might create a potential future in which humanoid dolls are (re)envisioned as therapeutic devices.

Experiments with Social Robots and the ‘Goodness’ of Artificial Sociality *Frederik Møller Vejlin, Aarhus University*

In this paper, I build on discussions of sociality and experimentation in social anthropology and STS to explore the creation of robots that technologically simulate aspects of human sociality. I draw on field research in Japanese robotics laboratories to question two assumptions made by researchers in social robotics and the field’s critics. The first assumption concerns the replication of human sociality in artificial systems. I suggest that it would be unwise to expect that social robots will perfectly simulate sociality and that this is a feature rather than a bug. Instead, researchers in social robotics and the robots they build might be experimentally enacting new forms of sociality and, in doing so, reconfiguring what sociality is and can be. I propose the concept of artificial sociality to capture both the on-going enactments and multiple results of such experimental reconfigurations. The second assumption concerns the professed ‘goodness’ of human social relations compared to our relations with robots. I suggest that an adequate notion of artificial sociality needs to include human-robot relations on the entire spectrum from ‘good’ to ‘bad’, just as we do in studies of relations between humans and other beings. I introduce examples of HRI experiments that trouble easy distinctions between good and bad relations and in doing so experimentally reconfigure the entangled relations between humans and robots that might produce artificial sociality. Finally, I show how attention to the experimental dynamics of artificial sociality contribute to existing discussions of human-nonhuman relations in anthropology and STS.

“I like my tech the way I like my girlfriend”: AI imaginaries and gender fantasies *Iliana Depounti, Loughborough University*

This presentation focuses on an AI companion (ro)bot, Replika, and how it is used by a subset of its subscribers to provide sexual/romantic intimacy. It explores the fantasies of users in a Reddit group about the AI girlfriend at the intersection of gendered and AI imaginaries. The research questions addressed are: what are the characteristics of the ideal (ro)bot girlfriend? What forms of companionship are valued by users? What are the characteristics of a good AI technology? Drawing on Bucher’s (2017) concept of the algorithmic imaginary and observations about the feminisation of AI voice assistants (Woods, 2018), the presentation examines how imaginings of a seamless AI experience intertwine with gendered fantasies. A thematic analysis of the Reddit discussion identified three themes: (i) the notion of the passive/unresponsive girlfriend/AI, (ii) a needy girlfriend/AI and (iii) the desire of users to control and tinker with the girlfriend/AI. The results of this study offer a better understanding of the relational dynamics (Guzman, 2018) with these technological artefacts and ultimately how these impact our “good relations” with machines.

Interviewing RealDollX – Mutually Felt Co-Constitution with a Sex:bot *Luise Erbenraut*

Using a combined theoretical frame of New Materialism and Affect Theory the notion of mutually felt co-constitution is made fruitful for an analysis of the intra-action with a sex:bot. It becomes a term to highlight the dependency of both constituents to feel each other bodily, sensorily, empathetically. Drawing from these theories I discuss how mutually felt co-constitution with a sex:bot shapes itself and ask whether the use of sex:bots might be a tool for individual self-empowerment among a diversity of participants. This approach aims to highlight the need for more visibility of queer desires in recent STS-research on sex:bots. For this purpose, I use the case of the app

“ReallDollX” and deduce the method of autoethnographic-anecdotes by means of a coalition of the posthuman method of interviewing digital objects, feminist autoethnography and tracing involved actors. The question if the app may be self-empowering for a diversity of people using it cannot be answered in general precisely because of these complex processes of emerging multiplicities, which are in turn accompanied by multi-layered streams of power. It needs to be addressed recurrently, situationally. Gender, sex and/or sexuality are becoming (in)visible and getting (re)compiled depending on the process of intra-action.

Session Organizers:

Andreas Bischof, University of Technology Chemnitz
Arne Maibaum, TU Berlin

021. Metaexpertise? STS, Metascience, and Data Science - I: The Technologies of Meta-expertise

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

The past decade has seen efforts to develop new forms of “domain-general” expertise such as metascience and data science. These have different motivations and intervene in specific fields in different ways—as interlocutors, partners, and, even, diagnosticians. Often, different forms of expertise establish distinct epistemic cultures in order to protect their autonomy and avoid the open conflicts that reveal rival epistemological commitments. However, interactions between domain-general and domain-specific forms of expertise have produced new conflicts. This raises challenging questions. Does the incursion of domain-general expertise represent a threat to the autonomy of disciplinary scientists? What would ‘good relations’ across this divide look like? How are domain-specific skills like embodied knowledge and practical judgment absorbed into domain-general systems meant to enumerate, evaluate, or automate scientific practice? The three sessions in this panel explore how these new “sciences of science” are transforming knowledge making.

Participants:

Data Science: Meta-Expertise or Interstitial Craft? *James Steinhoff; Anissa Tanweer, 2511 NE 165th St*

As a nascent field within the academy, the contours, attributes, and bounties of data science are currently indeterminate and contested. We studied how participants in an initiative to establish data science at a large U.S. research university defined data science and articulated their relationships to the field. We discuss the multiple and simultaneously held ways that data science was imagined among our research participants. One view, in keeping with broader popular discourses, casts data science as a form of meta-expertise that is agnostic and universally applicable to other domains of knowledge. Another view of data science, one that was far more prevalent among our research subjects, positions data science instead as emerging at the interstices of multiple domains. From this perspective, expertise in data science is a constantly moving target that requires collaboration, mobility, and an artisanal relationship with tools. We use Deleuze and Guattari’s explication of royal science versus nomad science to understand these competing views and explore the implications of this contestation for the present and future of data science in the academy.

Comparing Strategies for Universality in Cybernetics and Data Science *Przemyslaw Matt Lukacz, Columbia University, Department of Anthropology*

Sociologists of science have described both data science and cybernetics as “universal” disciplines. In this paper, I explore this idea by comparatively examining strategies for universality in cybernetics and data science. This focus is prompted by narratives that argue that many characteristics of data science have their precursors in cybernetics (e.g., Halpern, 2014). Commenting on Bowker’s work, David Ribes (2019) observed the resemblance between cybernetics and data science yet did not pursue this theme at length. My assessment of data science

universality is a direct response to Ribes’ views. More generally, my analysis adds to the ongoing conversations about how data science became “the megafauna of the academic landscape” (Crawford et al., 2014). This paper echoes Bowker’s 1993 examination of four strategies through which cybernetics became a “distributed passage point,” or a mediating discipline, through which domain research needs to pass through. In this form of meta-science, cyberneticians, similar to today’s data scientists, served as “translators” with a “black-boxed set of tools,” and yet indispensable to the work of other domains. The four strategies I explore are: 1) appropriations of universalizing discourse, 2) new divisions of labor, 3) institutionalization, 4) formation of big data as a mythology. This paper is based on ethnographic and interview data I gathered during research among data scientists and ecologists in 2019-2020. My methodology rests on the premise that it is crucial to simultaneously examine why data science seeks universal applicability and why other domains want to transition towards data-centric models of knowledge production.

Expectations And Expertise: Can STS And AI Benefit from each other? *Vassilis Galanos, University of Edinburgh*

During my doctoral research, investigating empirically and historically the interplay of expectations and expertise in the hype cycles of artificial intelligence (AI), I encountered the following research obstacle: conducting early literature review on the aforementioned topics, instead of STS articles investigating the social role of promise and legitimacy in shaping AI, scholarly search engines I used (ironically, AI-powered) returned technical articles about predictive software systems or knowledge-based expert systems. Often, articles about expert systems involved the question of prediction (as in medical diagnosis), which allowed me to reflect on the interplay between expertise and expectation, and how the problem of legitimacy influences not only decision making but also foresight strategies. Therefore, I came to observe patterns of similarity between the discipline I investigated (AI) and the discipline through which I investigated (STS). In this first public presentation of this observation, by focusing on the cognitive objects of “expertise” and “expectation,” I suggest that the contemporary maturity of AI and STS, reveals a common aim at apprehension and coding of knowledge structures; the former by the use of symbolic representations and statistical reasoning, and the latter by devising metaphors and narratives, inviting a novel alliance between the technical and the social.

Towards a Critical Technical Practice of Metascience:

Comparison Between 21st Century Data Science and 20th Century Information Science *Matthew Mayernik, National Center for Atmospheric Research*

Considerable debate exists today on almost every facet of what “data science” entails. Almost all commentators agree, however, that data science must be characterized as having an interdisciplinary or metadisciplinary nature. These arguments about current data science echo commentaries over the past century about information science as an interdisciplinary and metascientific research area, professional field, and grouping of skill sets and interests. This paper analyzes how data science and information science present a number of similarities: diverse participants and institutions, contested disciplinary boundaries, and diffuse core concepts. It uses the comparison between data science and information science to discuss three questions about data science going forward, focusing on issues of conceptual clarity, porous boundaries, and empowerment as a professional value. The historical comparison to information science suggests that the boundaries of “data science” will be a source of contestation and debate for the foreseeable future. Examining historical analogs for current “metasciences” like data science can help to build them into “critical technical practices” (Agre, 1997), that is, areas of work that actively examine and engage with their own limitations and inherent challenges. Agre, Philip E. (1997). Toward a critical technical practice: Lessons learned in trying to

reform AI. Social Science, Technical Systems, and Cooperative Work: Beyond the Great Divide, eds Bowker G, Star SL, Turner B (Mahwah, NJ: Erlbaum), pp. 130-157.

Session Organizer:

David Peterson, UCLA

Chair:

Martin Bush, University of Melbourne

022. Computational Media Technologies: Computing and Critique Beyond Disciplinary Configurations - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Despite the ongoing interest in the history, epistemology, sociology, and cultures of computing and its defining practices (see Benjamin 2019, Mackenzie 2001, Roberge & Castelle 2020), the study of computational media remains largely dispersed across a wide range of discipline specific venues. Inspired by the more systemic examinations of computing advanced by fields like critical AI studies, indigenous STS, and media anthropology, however, this open panel brings together scholars who share a similar interest in understanding the transdisciplinary complexities, alternative histories, and political a priori behind computational media. With that intention in mind, we propose to consider computation as a paradigmatic 'media technology' whose entanglement with questions of both mediation and technoscience promises to renew the study of technical cultures at large. Computational media, we contend, provides a rich, boundary (defying) object around which the disciplinary perspective of media studies, history of technology, and science studies can be made to converge. Not only does computational media relate contemporary technoscience to the cybernetic and cyborgial origins of computing (see Haraway 1985, Hayles 1999, Medina 2011), it also forces us to consider mediation as a structuring principle of technoscientific cultures, practices, and epistemologies (see Kittler 1986, Chun 2011). To explore these questions, this open panel will stage a number of interdisciplinary conversations which will not only revisit dominant discourses surrounding the study of computational media, but also challenge the disciplinary frameworks in which they have been historically concentrated.

Participants:

Cybernetic Model Work: Elegance and Observation Against Brute Force *William J Lockett*, *Massachusetts Institute for Technology (MIT)*

The cybernetics movement generated a discussion among scientists concerning the core epistemic virtues grounding knowledge claims for computational models of physical and biological phenomena. I argue that cybernetic practitioners sought ways to demonstrate how their models facilitated the sharing of epistemic virtues across engineering, mathematical, and empirical contexts while resisting "brute force." "Brute force," in this context, means throwing computational processing power at a problem without concern for whether that fact undermines the epistemic legitimacy of the result. My case study is Seymour Papert's work before 1970. I show that Papert criticized "brute force" not because he fundamentally opposed a neural network approach to AI but because he believed that there were epistemic costs associated with "hill climbing"—a common problem, related to "over fitting" curves, still prevalent in machine learning research. I show that Papert turned to empirical work with autistic children to coordinate elegance in mathematics with observation of learning. Like a psychoanalyst, he relied on "inference to best possible explanation" and what Husserl called "because thus" reasoning to explain how minds build repertoires of functions out of associative nets. Scholars have emphasized the ontological significance of cybernetics by assuming it's acceptance of the "black box." Cybernetic model work ought to be defined as a struggle for the variation of epistemic virtues against faith in brute force. Cybernetics grounds model making in a set of identifiable virtues that ward off brute force while managing its biological metaphors, taming them and it while fostering epistemic plurality.

"Looking into the Mind of a Neural Network": On the Institutional Underpinnings of AI's Empirical Turn *Théo Lepage-Richer*, *Brown University*

This paper proposes to locate the gradual displacement of biological plausibility by empirical successes as artificial intelligence's site of legitimacy (see Glorot and Bengio 2010; Hinton, Osindero, and Teh 2006) within the institutional and national context in which its current statistical form partially emerged. While symbolic AI and other approaches to machine intelligence are generally linked back to the military-industrial setting of American (Edwards 1996), British (Pickering 2010), and Soviet (Peters 2016) Cold War science, it is Canada's unique institutional context which provided the most conducive setting for AI's statistical form to survive and flourish while abandoned virtually everywhere else. Despite having been mostly devoid of any sophisticated computing capabilities until the mid-1970s, postwar Canada was the unlikely site of a wide range of debates and ideas around the nature and function of computational media. Starting with Pierre Elliott Trudeau's adoption of computing as a solution to both federalism and the modernisation of the state's bureaucracy (Trudeau 1965, 1969), the National Research Council and, later, the Canadian Institute for Advanced Research gradually articulated a computing policy anchored in the automation of specific administrative tasks (translation, coordination, resource management, etc.) fulfilled by state institutions. Echoing the work of Jon Agar (2003) and Edward Jones-Imhotep (2017) on the administrative underpinnings of computing, this project will provide a more granular and politically rooted account of AI's empirical conception of intelligence by revisiting the Canadian history of computer science and, more specifically, machine learning from the perspective of their financial and institutional support.

The Surface Tension of the Wall-Screen: The Network, the Great Firewall, and the Aesthetic of Non-Information *Jinying Li*, *Brown University*

If the network is understood as an open grid, then the wall is its containing surface. Such is the conceptual foundation of China's Great Firewall (GFW), a geoblocking system for Internet censorship. The censoring effect of the GFW is described as pingbi (screening), the word ping referring to an architectural object that is simultaneously a system of visual display and a device of spatial blockage, a material and functional overlap between a screen and a wall. The overlap informs the political meaning of the wall-screen as a mediating device that registers—metaphorically and structurally—the double logic of computer networks. The paper explores this duality by interrogating how the material and discursive formation of the wall-screen has informed the politics and aesthetics of information networks. I first trace the cultural formation of wall-screen in China's imperial history, where the positioning of ping was bound up with the symbolic function of socio-political hierarchy and dominance. I then examine how the meaning of wall-screen as a political symbol has shaped the computational construction and cultural imagination of the Great Firewall by shifting its designing philosophy from security to sovereignty. Lastly, I study how the duality of the wall-screen was channeled in the aesthetic response by examining the digital artworks by Miao Ying, who exploited the visible effects of the GFW's obstruction as a displaying surface for motion graphics. The result is what I call the aesthetic of non-information, for it addresses the unrepresentability of information by visualizing its negative state of concealment.

Making ICTs "Explained Iaras": Brazilian Modernism, Macunaima's Nostalgia, and Situated Histories of Computing *Alberto Jorge Silva de Lima*, *Celso Suckow da Fonseca Federal Centre of Technological Education*

The urgency for situated accounts on science and technology has been enacted in different forms by scholars in the fields of STS

and History of Technoscience, such as the proposal of going "beyond imported magic" as a way to acknowledge the multiple and diverse forms, contexts and directions associated with technoscience development in Latin America (Medina, Marques, and Holmes, 2014) or the proposal of a postcolonial computing as a set of pragmatic tactics to cope with computing in non-western countries (Philip, Irani, and Dourish, 2012). Following this thread, we present a dialogue with Brazilian Modernism, revisiting Mario de Andrade and his groundbreaking book *Macunaima* (1928), whose narrative enacts a situated and indigenous approach to the promises of modernity in the 1920s in terms of making the modern machines "Explained laras". These terms, we argue, evidence the Brazilian modernists' claims of surpassing nostalgia for a pre-modern or untouched national culture by locally constructing narratives of technoscience facts and artifacts, i.e., by granting them an ontology in the same way one would grant it to mythical entities such as the Brazilian *Iara*. Through the lens of this argument, we revisit the Brazilian promises of developing indigenous computing technology in the 1970s, especially how the first artifacts developed under these promises tried to enact discourses of local autonomy and national development without denying a dialogue with overseas knowledges, as an anthropophagical experiment similar to that predicted by Brazilian modernism in the 1920s.

Is All The World A Prediction? *Sun-ha Hong, Simon Fraser University*

What does it mean to imagine the world as predictions? To say that any social phenomenon can – and should – be predicted through large datasets and machine learning? I argue that such moralisation of prediction manifests computing technology's role as epistemic media. The mediation in question is not message transmission, but what Ian Hacking calls styles of reasoning: not whether big data and AI 'increase' our knowledge to fill in the positivist puzzle, or explicitly articulated tools like generative adversarial networks, but the underlying mood that articulates 'prediction' as a universal means for understanding bodies and lives. The analysis draws on multi-disciplinary scholarship on how the way we think about computers shape the way we think about human beings and their reasoning – including Katherine Hayles and Orit Halpern's critical histories of cybernetics, and Wendy Chun's work on the computational articulation of memory-as-storage. The default to prediction further concretises asymmetric power relations. As an example, I consider contemporary claims that 'criminality' can be predicted through face analysis. Building on critiques of this 'new physiognomy' by scholars like Os Keyes, I suggest that the obsession with prediction is not merely intellectual, but emerges to serve longstanding capitalist demands for the 'logistical life' (Julian Reid), in which to behave predictably for machinic measurements becomes a core requirement of a desirable and profitable subject. Prediction is typically feted as the reduction of risk: but as epistemic media, it designates a way of seeing in which we – the uncertainty latent in human living – are the risk.

Session Organizers:

Ranjodh Singh Dhaliwal, University of Notre Dame

Théo Lepage-Richer, Brown University

Chair:

Théo Lepage-Richer, Brown University

023. STS for Everybody

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

How can STS scholars spread their work and ideas outside of academia? In the last decade, STS has demonstrated a broad commitment to extending the rails of its scholarship. Yet even well-meaning tech activists like Tristan Harris and Cathy O'Neil have seemed unaware of even the existence of the field, much less the contributions it could make to public debates. And when STS scholarship does appear in popular works, such as in *Planet of the Humans*, things sometimes go off the rails. But the

interdiscipline has immense potential to help with impending crises, such as climate change or "post-truth" politics. At the very least, it is imprudent to allow scientific narratives proffered by people like Michael Shellenberger or techno-fixes proposed by Mark Zuckerberg to dominate the media. The purpose of this panel is to share knowledge and collaborate in imagining how STS trained people could be more effective "thoughtful partisans," how their research and analysis could more reliably influence policy debates. We are interested in panelists who can speak to: How to pitch STS-inspired op-eds to popular outlets? How to reach out to and work with journalists and documentary filmmakers? How to run a successful podcast or YouTube channel? Participants should be open to non-traditional panel formats, ones that allow more interaction and sharing with attendees. And we are particularly interested in contributions that emphasize learning from non-academics (not simply "informing" them) as well as engaging diverse audiences, especially across race, class, level of education, and political affiliation.

Participants:

We Live in Two Different Worlds: The Crisis of Expertise as an Ideological Controversy *David Caudill, Villanova University*

When the science concerning climate change, mask-wearing, or vaccinations becomes politicized, it loses its mooring in scientific evidence and impacts regulatory law. Counter-intuitively, the solution is likely not to insist on "cold, hard facts." Some level of modesty—regarding the uncertainties and probabilistic models of even the best science—is necessary to convince someone to change their scientific beliefs. Scholars who unwittingly idealize science, by emphasizing the anti-science ideology in the Trump administration, too easily ignored the ideological aspects of both sides in the crisis of expertise—that arrogance increases distrust of established science. While some have blamed STS for contemporary distrust of science, its modest view of science is likely one solution to the crisis of expertise. Science in policy contexts, unlike the results of a contested election, can rarely be characterized as involving unchanging "facts." Therefore, each side in the crisis of expertise should be understood as "believers" in their facts, not in the sense of deistic belief but rather as occupying a worldview. Drawing upon Wittgenstein and STS scholars inspired by his later philosophy, I identify four types of experts in the crisis of expertise—(i) consensus scientists, (ii) those who believe in consensus science, (iii) marginalized scientists, and (iv) those who hold marginalized scientific views. Expertise, that is, should not be associated with esoteric knowledge (or even correctness) but is rather the result of a community with shared practices and a common language. Recognizing these expert communities is a key to successful communication and scientific debate.

Against Modernist Illusions in Post-Truth Debates: Why We Need More Democratic and Constructivist Alternatives to Debunking Conspiracy Theories *Jaron Harambam, Institute for Media Studies - KU Leuven*

Various societal and academic actors argue that conspiracy theories should be debunked by insisting on the truthfulness of real "facts" provided by established epistemic institutions. But are academic scholars the appropriate actors to correct people's beliefs and is that the right and most productive thing to do? Drawing on years of ethnographic research experiences in the Dutch conspiracy milieu, I explain in this paper why debunking conspiracy theories is not possible (can scholars actually know the real truth?), not professional (is taking sides in truth wars what we should do?), and not productive (providing more "correct" information won't work as knowledge acceptance is not just a cognitive/epistemic issue). Instead of reinstalling the modernist legitimation narrative of science, I argue in this paper for an alternative that is both epistemologically stronger and sociologically more effective. Building from research and experiments with deliberative democracy in political science and epistemic democracy in STS, I propose to have "deliberative citizen knowledge platforms", instead of elite experts groups

alone, assess the quality of public information. Such societally representative bodies should enjoy more legitimacy and epistemic diversity to better deal with conspiracy theories and the broader societal conflicts over truth and knowledge they represent.

Session Organizers:

Taylor Dotson, New Mexico Tech

Michael Bouchey

024. Encounters with Failure in STS I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Science and Technology Studies has long focused on how knowledge is made and how publics are then enrolled in it. However, these past studies have often focused on successful articulations of knowledge; we argue that what is left behind, discarded or disputed is just as generative and important to research. While not exhaustive, these may include failures in policy, failures of pilot schemes or mundane failures in everyday life. Moreover, failure also occurs in relation to research processes. In research we can, for example, encounter absences in our data where perhaps we expected it to be. This can in turn make us unable to narrate and analyse the processes that enrol publics in the various failures that stand in relief to what becomes successful. What methods might exist or be developed to help discuss and analyse failure in the face of absent data, missing voices and actors for whatever reason we struggle to follow? This panel is primarily focused on the methods involved in researching failure or doing research in the face of failure or absence. As such, we invite papers that deal with one or both of these areas. We also welcome papers with a focus on digital methods or inventive methods. Due to the subject of the panel, we also encourage papers which reflect research projects at different stages of the research process. This panel aims to start and progress conversations amongst researchers about how conduct studies amongst failures and absences.

Participants:

Keeping It Together When Things Fall Apart: Lessons From the Social Construction/Destruction of Vaping *Amelia Howard*, *University of Waterloo*

In this presentation I explore failure as (1) an emergent research theme and (2) a practical problem, by reflecting on my experience studying the history and politics of e-cigarettes. I present findings from a case study of the technological system of vaping, and examine how this project, my research practices, and my position as an inquirer, changed when the technological system I was studying, began to fail catastrophically. Drawing from historical analysis of a variety of data sources, including, but not limited to user-generated content on vaping forums, youtube videos, e-commerce websites, public records, documents, and news, I discuss e-cigarette innovation as a user solution to failure to stop smoking and show how this in turn led to the growth of the vaping marketplace. I then consider the controversy over e-cigarettes and its emergence as the vaping system began to disrupt the ecology of tobacco products and tobacco problems, and engendered responses from established actors, industries (e.g. tobacco) and professions (e.g. tobacco control) and systems (e.g. behavioural health) within this ecology. Finally, I will show how this culminated in an intense, widespread moral panic, which set into motion the implosion of the vaping technological system. I conclude by reflexively discussing efforts to “keep it together” while studying a system that was falling apart in real time. I address problems of an increasingly volatile research site, disappearing digital records, hyper-proliferation of on-line content and how they were resolved (or not) and reflect on the emotional and intellectual difficulties - and pain - of bearing witness to failure, and how STS training helped me navigate this destabilizing experience.

Proprietary Chemicals in the FracFocus Database: Studying Absences, Inconsistencies, and Omissions *Grace Poudrier*, *Northeastern University*; *Sara Wylie*, *Northeastern*

University

Scientific research coupled with increasing public concern about the human and environmental impacts of fracking has led to partial disclosures of chemicals via an industry-sponsored database called FracFocus, established in 2011. FracFocus was designed to inform the public about fracking and provide oil and gas adjacent communities with information about the fracking chemicals used on or near their homes. FracFocus is notably a private website not subject to federal record laws, and all data is self-reported by individual companies. This paper considers how the absence of information from the database FracFocus can itself be studied as an object of empirical analysis. In particular, it examines how oilfield service companies benefit from intellectual property laws that permit the withholding of information about chemicals that companies deem as “proprietary” or as “trade secrets”, at their discretion. Building on prior works by Wylie (2018), Kinchy and Schaffer (2018), and Frickel (2014), we conduct a “big data” analysis of the presence, quantity, and locations of proprietary chemical records disclosed to FracFocus across 25 states over a ten year period, using an open-source version of the database called Open-FF. We take an agnotological approach to interrogate the construction of ignorance and legally sanctioned omissions in FracFocus data, seeking to generate new narratives for allocating corporate responsibility and accountability for previously opaque forms of chemical violence associated with fracking.

"We Found No Primates": Ethnography of An Unsuccessful Primatological Research *Paride Bollettin*, *Universidade Federal da Bahia*

The presentation will describe ethnographically an unsuccessful primatological research project conducted in northeast of Brazil. The project research group was composed of 3 primatologist led by a German University PhD student. The aim of the project was to study the behaviour of *Sapajus xanthosternus* in a protected and an unprotected areas, but in both places the research group has not been able to effectively encounter the primates groups. Consequently the project has been disbanded. The presentation will discuss this experience of unsuccessful research project focusing on two core directions. The first is the primate objectivation process that produced the distance between primatologists and *Sapajus*, despite various redefinitions of the research protocols. The second is a reflection on what STS can learn from analysing a failed research project with other-than-human primates. The thesis is that considering multi species agencies it is possible to observe how the success/failure divide is more related with subjectivities encounters that with specific research protocols.

Session Organizer:

Jessamy Perriam, IT University of Copenhagen

Discussant:

Katrine Meldgaard Kjaer

025. STS Underground Network Meetup

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Join us for an informal chance to connect participants from our past 4s-connected fieldtrips, workshops and panel sessions.

Session Organizers:

Abby Kinchy, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Jessica M. Smith, Colorado School of Mines

Chair:

Roopali Phadke, Macalester College

026. Global Health Futures and the Social Good I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:

Evidence-based development and the ambivalence of cost-effectiveness *Fiona Gedeon Achi*

This presentation explores the complex and at times ambivalent visions of the social good that animate “evidence-based development” by focusing on my interlocutors’ concern with cost-effectiveness. Evidence-based development is the movement to produce evidence about the effectiveness of anti-poverty programs and then using that evidence to shape efficient and effective policymaking in the Global South. It centers around the question of “what works”, on the randomized field experiment as the preferred pathway for producing knowledge, and on cost-effectiveness logics as the basis for adjudicating value and priorities. Drawing on fieldwork across Kenya, India and the USA with NGOs and research centers which work to transform global health pilot interventions into sustainable programs at large scale, this presentation examines how the preoccupation with cost-effectiveness makes visible calculations, but also multiple imaginations and aspirations, which exceed return on investment and business rationales. What does my interlocutors’ practice to introduce “moral weights” into cost-effectiveness models say both about a perceived inadequacy of common metrics used to guide decision making (such as the DALY) and the need to reckon with evidence-based development as more than an objective, scientific endeavor? How do my interlocutors’ ambitions to scale their sanitation program to “millions of people” merge in very concrete way –across slippery roads, broken dispensers, and shifting partnerships– a concern with cost efficiency but also the willingness to reach those whose are beyond the state’s basic infrastructure for living (Redfield 2012)?

Liberal Governance as Beaucrats’ Occupational Virtue in The Indonesian Welfare State *Daiki Ayuha, The University of Tokyo*

STS and its adjacent scholarships have been criticizing neoliberal infiltration into healthcare, such as an increasing public interest in the cost-effectiveness of medicine and the partial adoption of the market mechanism into state-controlled health service schemes. Contrary to such a popular view, this paper argues that the economization of medicine is not necessarily rooted in neoliberal values, by exploring how health technology assessment techniques are taught in the Post-Soeharto Indonesia. Indonesia has adopted a mandatory health insurance system in 2014, in which health service is provided by state-owned community health centers or public hospitals, and medical fees and insurance premiums are managed by a public legal entity. Under this scheme, it is technocrats who advocate for Big Government and the social rights that have increased and elaborated health financing techniques. As a channel for health economic knowledge and technique to spread, job training programs for local government officials play an important role. After the fall of the authoritarian regime, local government officials have started to play an increasingly important role in policymaking. Under the pressure of the anti-corruption movement and the merit system introduced after democratization, bureaucrats are urged to take many training programs. On these occasions, local government officials are taught health economic knowledge and techniques from health economics technocrats. For local government servants, these skills and knowledge are not only indispensable occupational ability, but also an embodiment of the value of clean corruption-free bureaucracy, which fits current-day Indonesian society.

Healthy Entrepreneurs’’: Visions of community health and the social good in Kenya *Ruth Prince, University of Oslo; Edwin Ambani Ambani Ameso, Aarhus*

In east Africa, “social enterprises” such as Healthy Entrepreneurs (founded 2011) are becoming increasingly prominent in health and development work. Critical of the NGO/donor model, which it holds as unsustainable, Healthy Entrepreneurs is funded through a mixture of corporate investment and philanthropic

capital and seeks to become self-sustaining through its model of enabling community health workers (CHWs) to become “community health entrepreneurs” (CHEs). It selects and trains particular CHWs in business management and offers them a loan and mobile phone from which they can order online selected commodities, including off-prescription medicines. The organization delivers these commodities to CHEs, who sell them to “community members” and use the small profit to pay off the loan and order more goods. These activities are integrated with the daily work of CHWS (e.g. visiting households, giving health advice, collecting statistics, and linking communities and the health system). In Kenya, Healthy Entrepreneurs is managed by staff deeply motivated by concerns about how to do development in what they see as a more “sustainable” way. While the model of turning community health workers into entrepreneurs is easily subject to critique, particularly because only few CHWs manage to become successful CHEs, we seek to understand the values and beliefs that undergird this approach. This paper thus traces the (at times ambivalent) perspectives, motivations and experiences of members of staff and the “healthy entrepreneurs” themselves concerning the relations between entrepreneurship, community health work, and the nebulous concept of the “social good”.

Session Organizers:

Sandra Bärnreuther, University of Lucerne

Ruth Prince, University of Oslo

027. Rethinking Outer Space And Science: Critical Engagements With The Cosmos And The Extra-terrestrial - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

Decolonising Modernity through the Cosmos: outer space imaginaries in Kazakhstan *Nelly Bekus, University of Exeter*

The proposed paper will discuss how elites and experts in semi-peripheral nations shape the debate on the development of national space programmes. Using the example of Kazakhstan the paper will explore kinds of political goals, societal objectives and social impacts are vested in outer space technopolitics by the political elites and experts of the country, how they communicate these ideas to their publics and what major scripts problematizing outer space development operate in public space. Post-Soviet Kazakhstan has inherited much of the outer space physical infrastructure created in the Soviet era, including its most powerful artefact - spaceport Baikonur, currently lend to the Russian Space Agency. In recent years, Kazakhstan developed its own ambitious program that involves both developing new space capabilities and gaining control over Baikonur in the future. Drawing on the case of Kazakhstan, this paper will discuss how the cosmic aspirations of postcolonial nations – despite tremendous constraints in terms of mobilising the resources required for building outer space capabilities – reveal the significance of outer space not only as an opportunity for innovative problem-solving, but also as an important instrument for reinventing national identities and re-asserting one’s position on the global modernity map. The paper will contribute to developing the emerging field of postcolonial outer space STS by investigating distinctive strategies for sense-making of outer space development in semi-peripheries.

The Extractive Gaze: Astronomical Southern Stations in South Africa *Osase Omoruyi*

For centuries, astronomers have turned their eyes and tools to the stars, studying the brightness and motions of the objects in our skies, and subsequently situating our lives in the cosmos’ context. Despite astronomy’s focus on the heavens, however, it remains inextricably linked to the politics that shape our lives on Earth. This paper briefly traces the history of astronomy in South Africa and its interconnections with imperialism, racism, and

capitalism—all of which characterized the British Empire's violent conquest of the Cape Colony in 1806. The British Empire's colonization efforts in the Cape Colony resulted in major astronomical progress such as John Herschel's detailed study of Halley's Comet, the satellites of Saturn, and stellar photometry. However, my focus lies not on those discoveries, but on the violent means through which those discoveries were obtained. From this historical grounding, I study 1900s South Africa and the ventures undertaken by American astronomers from institutions like Yale, Harvard, Columbia, and the University of Michigan to build southern stations for their observatories. In this paper, I use a framework of anti-colonialism to critically analyze observatory records and personal accounts from the astronomers involved in these extractive projects, in order to demonstrate the role of neo-colonialism in the construction and compilation of "Western" astronomical knowledge. Grappling with this history will allow us to situate the role of Eurocentric astronomy in the advancement of global racial capitalism, and think of what must be done to atone for this violence, while vehemently rejecting its continued expansion.

The Universe beside Itself: String Theory and the Question of Coloniality in Occupied Palestine *Jake Silver, Duke University*

The expanses of the sky have long provoked cosmological wonder about what may be out there and what humanity has yet to discover. Yet above the occupied West Bank, some of what invisibly hovers out there is common knowledge: from drones, to Israeli satellites wielding GIS technologies, to Israeli flags that the state is currently working to plant on the moon. While the sky has become a frontier for Israeli militarism, galactic curiosities are nonetheless skyrocketing in Palestine, with a number of astronomy institutions emerging across universities and NGOs. In this paper, I draw on ethnographic work with Palestinian astronomers and astrophysicists to unravel how the same scientific objects—planets, worlds, moons—also become objects of colonial conflict, offering Israelis and Palestinians new forms for understanding the relationships between colonizer and colonized, human and extraterrestrial, familiar and foreign. In particular, I take up one astronomer's declaration that string theory offers a political worldview because, just like strings in higher dimensions, Israeli colonialism imperceptibly yet powerfully inflects the everyday rhythms and tempos of scientific practice in Palestine. Israelis and Palestinian are so often discussed as if they live in two distinct worlds, yet here, string theory's colonial inflections entwine scientific knowledge with the multidimensional reaches of empire, the objective with the elusive. Paying attention to how the epistemological and the affective take shape together through astronomical work in the West Bank, this paper explores how colonial relations are braided into the sky, intimately reshaping political urgencies, attachments, anxieties, routines, and lives.

The Politics of Care in Outer Space *Reka Gal, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto*

Contemporary space colonization initiatives, including Jeff Bezos' Blue Origin and Elon Musk's SpaceX, legitimate their ventures as possible escape plans from planetary catastrophes. These narratives reinforce hopes of escaping responsibility for a planet in need of environmental restoration, thereby contradicting exit and survivalism with the work of maintenance and care. What remains unacknowledged in this framing of space colonization is that the lives of astronauts are dependent on maintaining their technological environment and caring for the spacecraft they inhabit. This paper argues that the making of good relations between humans and machines in outer space requires an ethics of care. In order to do so, I draw on news articles, interviews with astronauts, as well as NASA engineering and system reports, to conduct a material-discursive analysis tracing the themes of maintenance and care across historical accounts of space travel, with my site of analysis as the ISS. I

leverage insights from disability studies scholarship and from Indigenous environmental scholarship to reflect on the continuous reciprocity between the astronaut and the spacecraft, which are mutually responsible for caring for the other. I argue that therefore, rather than allowing for an escape from care and maintenance work, ensuring the normal operation of a spacecraft is a relevant analogy for how a relationship of care with the diverse ecological life support systems of Earth could be established.

Session Organizer:

Julie Michelle Klingler, University of Delaware

Discussant:

Eleanor Armstrong, University of Delaware

028. The algorithmic turn of prediction - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Throughout history, the future has been an important reference for mankind. Its role for life in the present, however, has changed significantly in the course of time. While the future was initially found to be unalterable, with the development of modern societies it became to be understood as an open horizon that stands in a causal relationship to the present – the future got shapable according to actions and decisions in the present. This shift in terms of interpreting the future made it even more attractive than before to produce knowledge about it. Predictive strategies subsequently flourished and technologies thereby played an increasingly important role. With the advent of modern forms of algorithmic data analysis, with machine learning and artificial intelligence gaining center stage, another shift in referring to the future is likely, presenting an exciting as well as urgent challenge for social sciences in general and STS in particular. Before this backdrop, this panel aims to discuss the theoretical as well as empirical implications of algorithmic prediction in the datified society. What effects does the algorithmization of prediction have on the systems, settings and situations concerned? How do algorithmic predictive technologies differ from their – allegedly less sophisticated – technological predecessors? And, last but not least, where are the analytical possibilities and limits of STS approaches regarding the algorithmic turn of prediction?

Participants:

Algorithmic Prediction: The Constitutive Process of Non-Human Decision Making *Jana Hecktor, Ruhr-Universität Bochum*

Machine learning systems are a fundamental part of our technological presence and play an important role in elaborate prediction practices. As a non-human actor they lay ground for human decisions and help minimize the insecurity that comes with pluralistic futures. However, these predictive algorithmic processes are also an essential part of machine decision making, in particular for those systems that interact directly with humans. Prediction of human actions helps reducing risk and uncertainty and therefore are essential for navigating and interacting with the world. During a human-machine interaction, the model trained on data from the past predicts simultaneously within the developing situation what the human is doing or asking to reduce the range of possible reactions. This leads to new machine centered processes of prognosis in the following way: The prognostic models are built to help machines decide, to reduce their risks and uncertainties. The possible futures are now created within machine processes and as such, are no longer directly accessible for the human. Though they're based on human influenced data and (partly) human created models - they are now basis for non-human decision- and prediction making processes. Following this idea, it seems necessary to take a look at these machine centered prognostic processes and to ask what changes when machine learning systems not only enhance existing probabilistic based prognostic models, not only serve as decision support systems for the human and their actions - but are used by machines themselves as internal guidance for their own actions.

Prediction as a shared accomplishment between humans and

machines – the case of peer reviewer selection *Felicitas Hesselmann, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies; J. Hartstein, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW)*

This contribution addresses the algorithmic turn of prediction by focusing on a case where prediction is not (fully) done algorithmically, but rather accomplished in a joined effort between human reasoning and algorithmic computation. Using qualitative (interviews) as well as quantitative (process-generated) data about the selection of peer reviewers at a biomedical publisher, it analyzes how this selection crucially hinges on the performance of a series of predictions of potential reviewers' timeliness, the quality of their feedback and the direction of their recommendation. Here, it can be shown that those predictions rely on data of past reviewer behavior stored in the editorial databases, as well as on quantitative performance assessments. At the same time, however, they are heavily influenced by intricate and often idiosyncratic interpretative processes performed by the individual editors. Editors evaluate potential reviewers along a number of complex criteria such as social relationships between authors and reviewers, epistemic preferences of particular reviewers, as well as overall composition and fit of the group of reviewers for one manuscript. Many of these interpretative tasks cannot be easily automated, and even if they can, such an attempt at automation is often conspicuously absent. As such, editors carve out a particular area of responsibility for themselves that stands apart from quantitative or algorithmic modes of assessment. Prediction thus is performed as a combination of both algorithmic and interpretative strategies.

The politics of algorithms. Designing a decision support tool for personalized medicine *Mauro Turrini, Consejo Superior Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC); Vincenzo Pavone, Consejo Superior Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)*

The focus of this presentation is a qualitative analysis of the design process of MSBioScreen, a medical decision aid algorithm inspired by the principles of personalized medicine in the treatment of multiple sclerosis patients. Traditionally, such tools have been used to standardize the trajectory of patients according to the dictates of evidence-based medicine. MSBioScreen, instead, stems from the desire to understand the specificities of the course of the disease of each patient through the combination of different types of data - clinical, biological, genetic, imaging - in order to find patients with similar cases and thus customize the prognosis and treatment. MS is a very unpredictable and potentially disabled disease. While there is no cure for MS, over the last two decades new pharmaceutical molecules have been introduced. In this context of great uncertainty, MSBioScreen aims to provide information that can: predict the trajectory of the disease, make the patient more involved in the process of prognosis and treatment, and, eventually, personalize the pharmaceutical treatment. This presentation intends to focus on the epistemological and material of the design process. On the one hand, this algorithm is immediately patented and becomes the core of a potential start-up. On the other, issues related to the access to data makes and the lack of a deterministic link with specific molecules make this algorithm did not allow a development corresponding to the initial ambitions of the algorithm.

Session Organizers:

Maximilian Heimstädt, Bielefeld University
Elena Esposito, Bielefeld University

Chair:

Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld

029. Toxic Goodness: Harmful Legacies, Hopeful Futures – I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

How do you cultivate good practices, relationships, and things in an environment of toxicants, toxic politics, and toxic relationalities? How do toxic production systems--based on extractivism, colonialism, and plantation capitalism--foment new forms of sustainability that cannot be excised from their deadly foundations? This open call examines urgent tensions between toxic legacies and hopeful futures when it comes to so-called renewable energies, green/blue/bio-economies, waste management systems, and sustainable agriculture/aquaculture. Such hopeful alternatives to unsustainable production systems hold within them the possibility of working towards a "Greater Good," however, "goodness" is largely built on toxic colonial and capitalist foundations that are rendered invisible through sustainability discourse. In other words, in making sustainable things or practices, toxicities in many forms are in fact often sustained. This panel will therefore investigate the ways scientists, investors, and producers in the agricultural, aquacultural, and waste sectors build on toxic legacies as they seek to render generative material processes--such as photosynthesis, bioremediation, and fermentation--into sustainable tools. We encourage papers that empirically illuminate how social systems and material processes together shore up, generate, and maintain toxicity. Such investigations will open space to question whether and how good relations could be cultivated out of toxic relationships without assuming toxicity can be entirely expunged. The overall aim of this open panel is thus to critically address how sustainable processes depend on toxic production systems, as a first step towards activating better ways of living amid toxicity.

Participants:

"Your Home is Your Biosphere": Legacies of Gender and Race in the Domesticity of Alternative Technology *Emma Schroeder, University of Maine*

When Sean Wellesley-Miller argued that "your home is your biosphere" in 1977, the alternative technology movement had garnered support from grassroots activists, national governments, and international agencies. Proponents imagined that constructing alternatives to ecologically destructive technological systems could not only solve earthly peril but provide social revolution (Winner 1986). In many ways, this movement presaged current discussions over sustainability. However, just as Myles Lennon has shown that today's infrastructure justice proponents reify racial social orders (Lennon 2020), alternative technology constructed sustainable spaces not for any body, but for specifically raced and gendered bodies. Imagining homes as biospheres inscribed white, heteronormative, middle-class hegemonic domestic practices into ecological-technological systems intended to preserve a threatened earth. This paper argues that these raced and gendered practices allowed such technologies to be used in development projects, exporting social orders along with technological interventions (Jasanoff 2004). Thus, this paper extends recent scholarship on management of the global environment through population control by arguing that such geopolitical projects included control of women's domestic practices, not only their reproductive lives (Murphy 2017, Sasser 2018). However, while the toxic legacies of white domesticity as a form of colonial power (Stoler 2002) remained latent in these eco-technological designs, the women who participated in such groups began to assert various forms of political power that did not conform to existing structures. They insisted on new forms of technoscientific citizenship (Kimura 2016) and shared public concern for harms, providing a space of political openness rather than the closure of private domestic acts.

Multispecies Mending: Microbial Factories, Circular Bioeconomies, and Fermentation to Fix (the) Carbon (Cycle) *Eleanor Hadley Kershaw, University of Nottingham*

Microbial capacities for material transformation are increasingly mobilised to repair damaged ecologies at a range of scales. In synthetic biology and industrial biotechnology, the development of 'microbial factories' for the conversion of various feedstocks into materials, chemicals, fuels and food is heralded as a means of addressing climate change, reducing societal reliance on fossil

resources, and creating circular bioeconomies. While social studies of synthetic biology have explored promissory discourses (e.g. Schyfter and Calvert, 2015) and factory metaphors (e.g. Boudry and Pigliucci, 2013), less attention has been paid to the potentially generative chemo-socio-material relations and resource-making enacted by microbial factories and their non-human labour. This paper explores multispecies collaboration towards material, chemical, social and ecological transformation in the case of a European research project developing three new microbial factories in an integrated waste treatment platform in Italy. The researchers and companies involved aim to engineer microbes to (more efficiently) use carbon dioxide to produce value-added chemicals and bioplastics. Through the microbial labour of gas fermentation, waste gains worth as gas feedstocks are transformed into commercially valuable materials, fixing carbon and offering 'sustainable' chemical production and waste treatment processes. Drawing on ethnographic engagement with this project, the paper opens up microbial factories to investigate the multi-scalar collaborations and transformations they (might) entail. It interrogates tensions between logics of biocapitalism and of industrial reparation, asking whether microbial factories are best understood as ecomodernist technofixes that lock in toxic regimes, or as the becoming 'ecologically obliged' (Papadopoulos, forthcoming) of waste treatment and chemical industries.

Toxic Nutrients: The Politics of Harmful Algal Bloom Mitigation in Lake Erie *Gebby Keny, Rice University*

Each summer, several hundred square miles of Lake Erie's southwest basin are covered in a toxic pea-green slime that threatens drinking water supplies and depletes oxygen levels within lake waters, causing mass wildlife die-offs. These increasingly common and disruptive events are referred to as harmful algal blooms (HABs) and have been historically associated with the leaching of nutrient fertilizers applied to farm fields in northwest Ohio. There, vast wetlands located within Ottawa Nation territories once stood and regulated the flow of nutrients throughout the landscape, before they were violently cleansed of inhabitants, drained, and converted into the flat agricultural landscapes associated with the region today by white settlers in the mid-19th century. Through careful attention to the infrastructures, knowledges, and histories that interlace Lake Erie's watershed, this paper considers the relationship of contemporary HAB mitigation efforts carried out by agricultural experts and wetland scientists to longstanding political and material arrangements that have marked the conditions of possibility for life and death throughout the region. Notably, it explores such relations through an analysis of these actors' engagements with "legacy nutrients"—nutrients which accumulate in farm soils at unknown volumes and dissolve into waterways at rates varying from one year to one century—as they work to develop a comprehensive budgetary model of contemporary nutrient inputs and outputs throughout Lake Erie's watershed. Ultimately, the paper aims to recuperate an imagination of HABs that thinks beyond embodied encounters with algal toxins and is firmly rooted within contested and lively settler-colonial terrains of harm.

Toxic Ash, Hopeful Leaves: Brazilian Sugarcane Histories and Biofuel Futures *Katie Ulrich, Rice University*

Sugarcane scientists and industry actors in Brazil are working to expand the volume and scope of sugar-based fuels, chemicals, and other materials like bioplastic. They aim to reduce reliance on fossil fuels and mitigate problems like global warming through this versatile plant. Colonizers brought sugarcane to Brazil five hundred years ago and its cultivation, first through slavery and later through waged but brutal labor, is infamous for its intense and deadly conditions, as well as negative environmental impact. These dark histories are sometimes acknowledged, sometimes distanced from present practices, and sometimes reframed (one could say sugarcoated) as a source of

tradition, knowledge, and experience for producers. This paper specifically starts with memories of toxic sugarcane ash, which rained down when cultivators burned fields to facilitate manual harvest, filling streets, homes, and lungs with harmful particulates. Today, with mostly mechanized harvesting, the cane leaves that previously combusted into ash are now being studied by scientists as a new source for even more sugar that could be extracted from the crop. Such technological advancements would increase sugarcane's efficiency as a feedstock for renewable materials. With this molecular reconfiguration of this particular source of sugarcane toxicity, what toxicities still remain, and what new ones are created? Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork and historical documents, this paper ultimately takes sugarcane ash/leaves as an entry point into thinking more broadly about the multiple toxicities of sugarcane histories (such as toxic land use, labor, and masculinity) and how they are addressed and negotiated in contemporary renewable efforts.

Session Organizers:

Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University
Jessica Caporusso, York University
Katie Ulrich, Rice University

Chair:

Jessica Caporusso, York University

Discussant:

Zoe Wool, University of Toronto

030. Relations and Troubles of Tools of Valuation – I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

Academic CVs as media of scholarly subjectification *Markus Tumelshammer, University of Klagenfurt*

In my research I analyse how epistemic subjects (Knorr-Cetina 1999) are produced through multiple quantitative and qualitative valuation practices involving academic CVs. Actors who read and evaluate CVs as "tools of assessment" (Ruth 2008) do not only have to tackle the question whether the person presented in the CV is suitable for a given post, but also whether, and on the basis of which criteria CVs can be interpreted in the first place (Kaltenbrunner/De Rijcke 2019). Beyond applications, strategically aiming to obtain academic positions or funding, academic CVs also represent epistemic subjects on homepages of institutions, in academic social networks or in personal archives. In my talk I will discuss findings from my research work, including interviews with historians, members of appointment committees, equal opportunity committees, and field observations. My research suggests that for some authors of CVs, counting and accumulating items can be pleasurable. Others engage in creating CVs of failure (Stefan 2010), problematizing aspects otherwise kept rather silent within the logics of "epistemic capitalism" (Fochler 2016). Altogether, practices of presentation and valuation associated with academic CVs have in common that they require addressing various forms of (imagined) others – e.g. explicit or tacit scales, referees, scientific subfields and their norms, ideals and personae. This implies taking over different perspectives and adopting expectations attributed to these others, in order to look at and make comparative judgments about the qualities and quantities of the respective academic self. Thus, I understand academic CVs as media of scholarly subjectification.

Becoming Excellent: Exploring Researchers' Practices of Valuation When Applying for ERC Starting and Consolidator Grants *Mallory James; Ruth Müller, MCTS TU München*

Practices of applying for research funding are omnipresent and highly important processes in academic work. Yet, there have been so far been no systematic studies that analyze how

researchers engage in these practices and how these practices impact their self-understanding and the orientation of their work. This constitutes a both significant gap in research in the social studies of science and in reliable knowledge for science policy making. In this talk, we share first insights from a project that aims to address this gap by studying how researchers engage in practices of valuation as they apply for Starting and Consolidator Grants from the European Research Council ERC. We have chosen the ERC as a focus point for this study because it is a highly influential funding organization that increasing numbers of researchers apply; and because its model of research (e)valuation increasingly serves as a blueprint for the (re-)organization of peer-review practices at other funding councils. The projects employs a three-pronged approach to understanding researchers applications practices: 1) reflexive peer-to-peer interviews with researchers that discuss their application strategies while they are awaiting evaluation results 2) interviews with coaching and support staff that advise researchers during their application processes as well as participant observation at coaching events and 3) a discourse analysis of researchers' application documents. Thereby, we aim to reconstruct socio-epistemic practices in which researchers construct value in their applications and the relationship between these practices and the emergent normative infrastructures that surround and advise their practices.

Deep matters: making research in the deep ocean valuable *Sarah Rose Bieszczad, Centre for Science & Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University; Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna; Sarah de Rijcke, Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS)*

Ocean science is called upon to aid in solving grand societal challenges, like the declining health of the ocean and climate change. This call is reflective of larger shifts in evaluation systems and practices towards valuing impactful, interdisciplinary, solution-oriented research, with policy makers increasingly embracing the idea that directed science policy can help tackle 'grand challenges' facing society. These steering efforts may relate to or create tensions with other benchmarks for scientific quality, e.g. excellence or global competitiveness. For example, Horizon Europe's mission-oriented framework aims to be widely relevant to society; to be targeted, measurable, and time-bound; and to establish impact-driven goals, while simultaneously being based upon a market-shaping framework that steers research along economic principles. Choices in structuring research priorities may affect research fields differently: formalizing the inclusion of social impact into research evaluations may produce different orders of worth, wherein ocean research fields fare differently based upon their ability to construct societal relevance. This shift could potentially create tensions for ocean science fields that seem to have an epistemic focus which is distant from societal concerns. Through interviews, this paper will examine how researchers in two such deep ocean fields—paleoceanography and deep sea geomicrobiology—navigate multiple, potentially incongruous orders of worth. For example, when applying for funding how do researchers navigate simultaneous demands for their research to be relevant both to society and challenges it faces as well as to their scientific communities?

Sculpting Boundaries: Standards, quality and value in artistic research *Alison Gerber, Lund University*

Issues of quality and value are perpetually lively and contentious in academic work, and research on the architecture of evaluation has consistently shown that organizational constraints, whether well-motivated or adopted ad hoc, have enormous influence on outcomes. The negotiations behind the development of standards are especially decisive in new and emerging disciplines; historical work on disciplinarity and the development of the academy offers important conceptual and theoretical frameworks,

but it is unclear how such processes might have changed in a modern academic context marked by increasing quantification and competitive national and supranational funding. This paper takes as its case the recent development of the state-funded field of artistic research and the PhD in artistic practice in Sweden, where the interplay of artistic, scientific, and public standards and values is pushed front and center with each funding cycle and public viva. Drawing on an analysis of documentary evidence (dissertations, evaluation committees' assessments, hiring decisions, and funders' reports), this manuscript shows how diverse tools of valuation are mobilized by insiders (artists, artistic researchers, art school faculty) and outsiders (faculty and researchers from other disciplines, funders) in the development of standards and boundaries in the the artistic research field. With special attention to those judged not good enough, and the justifications offered by those who reject them – for research funding, for entrance to doctoral programs, and for the PhD degree – this analysis will leverage unique sources to understand the interplay between valuation processes, internal and external standards, and outcomes in emerging academic disciplines.

The feeling rules of peer-review: how reviewers define, display and manage emotions in evaluation for research funding *Lucas Brunet, Munich Center for Technology in Society (MCTS); Ruth Müller, MCTS TU München*

Application for high-level funding is a situation of stress among applicants in competition for scarce funding, and of possible conflicts between reviewers about how to value different proposals. Although the norms regulating the practices of research evaluation have been previously described, little is known about how these norms operate emotionally. In this talk, we draw on the sociological concept of feeling rules to investigate how emotional norms govern the functioning of peer-review evaluation for high-level funding. We investigate which emotions are supposed to be expressed, displayed and regulated by reviewers and applicants, and how these emotions relate to the structural organisation of peer-review. Our presentation reconstruct these feeling rules by studying the Starting and Consolidator grants of the European Research Council and Individual Fellowships of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, two European funding mechanisms which offer contrasting perspectives on the organisation of grant evaluation, organised in face-to-face or online panels. We analyse peer-to-peer interviews conducted with members of the review panels and reviews written on diverse European Research Council proposals. The argument of our presentation is that the work of proposal evaluation requires emotional labor to comply with a set of feeling rules that are central to the functioning of these panels and that also affect how applicants are evaluated. In particular, we show that these feeling rules concern the emotions that reviewers are allowed to express, as well as those that applicants are expected to show.

Procedural care: Licensing practices in animal research *Tone Druglitrø, TIK Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture, University of Oslo*

This paper provides insight into the entangled and flexible, yet tensed relations between techniques of governance, accountability and care in animal research. A consistent critique against animal research has been a lack of openness and transparency. In the recent decade, this concern has been integrated in practices of licensing animal research. In Norway, which forms the empirical site of this paper, the licensing system has undergone significant revisions drawing closely upon EU directives, in which a central aim is to 'foster a culture of care'. In a Norwegian context, this means that in order to facilitate animal research scientists and public officials must mobilize a set of politico-legal devices such as harm-benefit analysis. These devices are designed to respond to different ethical concerns that cuts across science, society, and the regulatory system, and work

as tools of accountability and transparency. The paper traces these tools and devices and explore how care and accountability is articulated and negotiated, in what form and through what procedures. The paper concludes that the licensing system for animal research forms a specific genre of care – procedural care – that holds promise and potential for bringing together and more openly engaging with care(s) in conflict. A main aim in the paper is to demonstrate the potential of “care” as an analytical concept in STS to study valuations as well as ethical-political tensions in and across bureaucracy, science, and culture.

Session Organizers:

Kristin Asdal, TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture

Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna

Chair:

Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech

031. Critical and Reflexive Perspectives on Conferencing as Scientific Practice - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Academic conferences are prime sites of exchange in global science. As events where face-to-face or digital encounters occur, they represent important nodes of knowledge circulation, and serve as spaces of research communication, academic identity formation, and networking. ‘Conferencing’ is recognised as an essential activity for building an academic career, which is manifested through the inclusion of conference participation and organisation in recruitment and promotion criteria. Conference participation, however, frequently requires access to resources that are distributed highly unequally – such as funding, visas, work-place permission, family support, and freedom from care responsibilities for the duration of an event. As such, academic conferences are sites of privilege and disadvantage, which may reinforce social inequalities in relation to gender, nationality, race/ethnicity, social class/caste, disability, language, and other intersecting dimensions of difference. This panel critically interrogates conferencing as scientific practice and its structuring effects in academia. It comprises contributions that offer theoretical conceptualisations, empirical studies and critical reflections on conference practices and their impact on maintaining/reproducing inequalities in the scientific field. Despite growing interest in conferences and an expanding evidence base revealing their adverse social and environmental effects, they remain a niche subject in the social studies of science. The panel seeks to provide an integrative discursive space to stimulate the formation of a scholarly network for future exchange, linking STS with higher education research and gender studies. The panel consists of two sessions, whereby this second one focuses on online conferences during and after the pandemic, with contributions weighing the positive and negative effects of meetings in virtual space.

Participants:

Conferences as Scientific Practice: What Do Responses To Covid Reveal About Disciplinary Differences **Rob Evans**, Cardiff University; **Harry Collins**, Cardiff University; **Rachel Hale**, Cardiff University; **Shannon N. Conley**, James Madison University

The bans on travel – both within and between countries – introduced in response to the global covid-19 pandemic have had a profound effect on scientific conferences and meetings. Many in-person conferences and meetings have moved online, whilst others have been cancelled completely. For some, this is seen as a positive development, with a bloated conference industry being cut down to size and the success of online events marking the start of a transition away from environmental cost of the international conference and the inauguration of a new, more inclusive, format in which travel costs are no longer a barrier to participation. For others, however, the demise of the in-person conference introduces new forms of inequality and prevents the tacit knowledge needed to build collective identity and scientific consensus from being shared. In this paper, we report on the

early stages of a project that records how the suspension of in-person meetings for most of 2020 was experienced by scientists working in the physical and biosciences. We identify their pre-pandemic patterns of conference going and explore the differing views of scientists on the costs and benefits of in-person and virtual conferences. In addition to the expected within-group differences, we will also explore the possibility of between-group differences and the extent to which these can be related to differences between the epistemic cultures of the physical and biological sciences

Who Can Go to the Conference? An Undergraduate Perspective on Access and Career Paths **Maxwell Etka**, James Madison University

Questions of access and inclusion with respect to academic conferencing should consider early career researchers, particularly undergraduate and graduate students, whose ability to participate in conferences is both crucial to their career trajectories and typically limited by resources. Their exclusion can additionally contribute to a lack of perspectives on the topics of focus. As an undergraduate STEM student participating in the STS Futures Lab at James Madison University, my knowledge of conference proceedings through self-experience does not extend far, but through a combination of autoethnographic reflections and interviews with undergraduates, graduate students, and junior faculty who have gone to conferences both within and outside STS, this paper will reflect on the structure, conceptualization, obstacles, and overall access of academic conferences that may lead to biases and inequalities. This project will also draw on interviews with participants at the student-led STGlobal conference in Spring 2021. Drawing on the concept of the Matthew Effect, and combining interview data with analysis of broader trends in academic conferencing, this paper will also consider the potential opportunities and constraints of online conferencing on junior scholars. In a world more that has restricted travel and human contact than ever, who is able to go to academic conferences? What lessons can be learned going forward?

What is This Event For? Lessons from Conferencing at 3am in Amsterdam, and Other Venues **Natalia Kovalyova**, iSchool UT Austin

Academic conferences are usually hailed as prime sites for knowledge production and exchange. But they also perform multiple auxiliary functions beside research presentations, round table discussions, and author-meet-the-public sessions. Large conventions typically accommodate book exhibits, professional membership meetings, job fairs and recruitment events, award ceremonies, and, of course, massive networking. To a novice, this abundance might look excessive, but to a seasoned scholar, they constitute an infrastructure indispensable to the maintenance of professional identities as knowledge makers. With the onset of COVID-19 and restriction on in-person gatherings, it is important to ask what provisions, features, and affordances can be leveraged to sustain this relational infrastructure. What new formats can help create spaces and opportunities that sustain feelings of belonging to a community of scholars? Which conference experience cannot migrate online? And what these affordances and solutions teach us about the contexts and conditions of contemporary knowledge production? My presentation seeks to answer these questions by analyzing programming choice of eight virtual conferences convened in 2020, ranging from national conventions of professional organizations to graduate student symposia. It examines them from three perspectives: as a speaker/presenter; as an attendee; and (to a lesser degree) as an organizer – and draws on theories of information and communication behavior to highlight the constants, the variables, and the currently unknowns of the ongoing adjustment of conferencing as a knowledge practice. The presentation will conclude with tips on how to make the most out of conferencing in the “new normal.”

Session Organizers:

Susanne Koch, Centre for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University

Emily Henderson, University of Warwick

Nidhi Sadana Sabharwal, National Institute of Educational Planning and Administration (India)

Rob Evans, Cardiff University

Chair:

James Burford, La Trobe University

032. (Re)configuring care practices in pandemic times I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Care practices were addressed in STS by Annemarie Mol (2002, 2008, 2010) as capturing a specific way of engaging with material reality as well as framing situated human relations. Hence, care bears not only upon intimacy or affectivity, but relates to forms of interdependency between ontology and normativity (“ontonorms”; Mol 2012). The session starts from and further develops the discussions on relevance of care practices focussing on the (re)configurations of care practices during the COVID-19 pandemic. Such a discussion of „care“ takes up not only a currently highly relevant social topic, but also acknowledges the salient empirical shaping of theoretical reflections on care in STS as ways of handling reality and transforming social relations. While COVID-19 differently addresses virologists, clinicians, physicists, epidemiologists, immunologists, or economics (Mol and Hardon 2020), a wide range of practices of care proliferated in response to the health crisis beyond these formal and mainstream settings, draw mainly on spatial (and social) proximity (neighbourhoods, peer-groups), and emphasised a temporal continuity of the caring engagement (regular visits, extended homeschooling). In a word: specific (re)configurations of care are rendered visible in dealing with personal concern, vulnerability, and (inter)dependence (Kittay 2015). The session includes contributions on: – expertise negotiated along care practices; – care related to groups traditionally framed as disadvantaged: elderly, people with disabilities, indigenous people, and other culturally diverse groups; – goods shaping actors understanding of care; – alliances of human and non-human entities as modes of pragmatic coping with pandemic crisis; – methodological adjustments regarding (re)configurations of care.

Participants:

“I’m More Comfortable Talking in Person”: (Re)Enacting Care within Distanced Ethnographic Methods *Charlotte Waltz, University College Cork; Kelsey Marr, University of British Columbia Okanagan*

The first year of the COVID pandemic has encouraged major methodological shifts in ethnographic reproduction research. Social-distancing and lockdown regulations in many countries have forced a turn to distanced ethnographic methods (i.e. interviews via Zoom; online participant observation). Such spatial and physical separations have been imposed in the name of care. Yet, we have found that this shift poses major challenges for researchers working in fields which require researcher-interlocutor relations prefaced on care and caring practices. Social scientific research on reproductive experiences necessitates sensitive and affective relationships among researchers and interlocutors, due to the highly personal nature of the topic (Rapp 1999). In this paper, we draw upon our on-going ethnographic research on abortion in Ireland and reproductive disruptions in Sweden in which we have adopted distanced ethnographic methods. We discuss how we navigate the tension between the care practices necessary to our sensitive research topics and distanced ethnographic methods. We argue that distanced ethnographic methods do not simply allow normative embodied care practices to continue, but rather that care must be mutually (re)enacted and (re)configured (Mol 2002) through the networked relationships among researchers, interlocutors, and non-human technological agents. The negotiation of care and care practices is rooted in the situated knowledges (Haraway

1988) of all of the actors in play. As such, distanced ethnographic methods must themselves be (re)configured in order to (re)enact care within these research relationships.

Legacies Online and Left Behind: Reconfiguring Hospice Palliative Care under Pandemic Conditions *Jessica Bytautas, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, University of Toronto; Pia Kontos, KITE-Toronto Rehabilitation Institute, University Health Network; University of Toronto; Blake Poland, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, University of Toronto; Kristin Bright, Middlebury College; University of Toronto*

The COVID-19 pandemic has seen an unprecedented shift to digital remote care across health sectors. In this paper, we consider the implications of these transformations for a volunteer-based hospice organization in Toronto, Canada that, prior to the pandemic, provided in-person services in home and community care settings. Drawing on insights from Karen Barad and new materialisms theory, we explore the impact of the pandemic on end-of-life legacy work and its entanglements of human/non-human materiality, agency, and care. Legacy work consists of inviting patients to reflect on their lives, what matters most to them, and how they wish to be remembered. Positioned by its proponents as an antidote to existential suffering, legacy work is increasingly prevalent in both medical and commercial end-of-life practices. However, recent critiques suggest that these practices oversimplify the complexity and diversity of end-of-life experiences, and privilege western neoliberal ideals regarding family and capital. This paper starts with a discussion of legacy projects, what they are and who they are for, and then turns to the contemporary pandemic context. How are particular norms about death and life reproduced or revised in legacy work? How does digital remote care impact the intention or shape of legacy projects? We conclude with a discussion of the implications (some realized, some yet-to-be-seen) of this new care regime for volunteer-patient relationality and “suffering together with.”

Multispecies Care Across a Pandemic Anthropocene *Sofia Varino, University of Potsdam*

What are the historical links between environmental care and healthcare? From the early days of the pandemic, theories about the nonhuman origin of the novel coronavirus and cross-species transmission were prevalent, bringing to the fore concerns about deforestation and loss of habitat, as well as environmental pollution and access to healthcare. In this paper, I seek to address these concerns by examining them historically in terms of care using a transdisciplinary cultural studies methodology that challenges strict divisions between the humanities and the social and natural sciences, seeking to generate connective tissue among disparate disciplinary locations. Moving beyond clinical and/or biomedical implications of care, I examine its convoluted ecological dimensions in terms of “bodily burdens” (Chen, 2020) in relation to environmental and racial justice contexts. My paper thus participates in the necessarily transdisciplinary fields of medical and environmental humanities and the emerging field of multispecies studies, which poses the unsettling question: “What does it mean to live with others in entangled worlds of contingency and uncertainty?” (Dooren, Kurksey, Münster, 2016). Grappling with the notion of multispecies care by tracing genealogies of the coronavirus pandemic where the clinical and the ecological have converged, my paper considers how such genealogies demand the decentering of a normative “human” approach to care while proposing a reorientation towards transformative modes of caring for a multiplicity of life forms and life worlds.

Transnational care collectives in the COVID19 pandemic *Tanja Ahlin, University of Amsterdam - AISSR*

How to care for aging parents when family members are asked to physically distance from each other? How to be a ‘good daughter’

or a 'good son' in the pandemic when what are generally considered key care practices, such as visiting, are not possible? Drawing on long-term ethnographic fieldwork among Indian transnational families, I use the material semiotic approach to analyze how family members incorporate everyday information and communication technologies (ICTs) in care. I argue that parents, their children and the technologies form 'transnational care collectives' through engaging in particular care practices. In this context, the norms of what it means to be a 'good child' shift from being grounded in practices that require physical proximity (e.g. intergenerational co-residence and cooking) to practices that can be done at a distance, such as frequent calling. In pre-pandemic times, regular visiting and sending remittances were additional ways through which Indian migrants could be enacted as 'good children'. As a consequence of the pandemic socioeconomic reorganization, these two practices have become increasingly difficult due to travel restrictions and loss of employment, while the use of ICTs to maintain caring relations has intensified. In this presentation, I build on pre-pandemic fieldwork and on new data to discuss the impact of the pandemic restrictions on transnational care collectives and filial norms in Indian transnational families.

Session Organizer:

Cristina Popescu, EHESS - Centre d'Etude des Mouvements Sociaux

Discussant:

Stefan Nicolae, University of Trier

033. Doing and Making Times I: Multispecies

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Participants:

Mediating More-Than-Human Times: The Case of the Great American Chestnut Tree *Elaine M Gan, New York University*

This paper explores ways of engaging more-than-human, more-than-European temporalities by focusing on the case of the American chestnut tree (*Castanea dentata*), the beloved "queen of forests" in the Eastern United States until the 19th century. In the early 1900s, billions of American chestnut trees succumbed to fungal blight disease from Georgia to Maine when plant nurseries in New York began importing trees from Asia. Japanese and Chinese chestnuts (*C. crenata* and *C. mollissima* respectively) happened to carry a ravenous hitchhiker, the bright orange fungus (*Cryphonectria parasitica*). The death of American chestnuts over the last two centuries has changed and continues to change lives, livelihoods, institutions, and landscapes. In recent years, geneticists at the State University of New York (SUNY ESF) have genetically modified "restoration trees," blight-resistant versions of the American chestnut. In 2020, applications are pending for states to permit the planting of these transgenics throughout the East Coast. Multiple groups, ranging from the American Chestnut Foundation to Indigenous (Haudenosaunee and Onondaga) nations, park managers, environmental ethicists, and independent tree lovers, gather around this story. Intersecting histories, socialities, and futurities are brimming with temporalities of matter, media, and meaning. By attending to the multiple ways in which time is being made and unmade, connected and disconnected, synchronously and asynchronously, I argue for richer approaches to analyses of science, technology, and society. Theoretically and methodologically, I engage with the "ontological turn" in feminist and de/postcolonial studies of technoscience, including Barad, Mol, Tsing, and Kohn.

Of Bread and Time: Temporal Mending Practices Under Quarantine *Andrea Alarcon, University of Southern California; Maria Soledad Altrudi, University of Southern California; Frances Corry*

The pandemic has brought competing understandings of time to the fore as people everywhere grapple with slippery sensations of

temporality. Do we have an abundance of time, with few plans to fill it? Is time the same as it always was, with the calendrical march of rent checks and bills due? Or has time sped up with its ever-greater demands, from homeschooling children to back-to-back teleconferencing? Taking the COVID-19 crisis as a fruitful context to explore contending discourses of time vis-a-vis fluctuating notions of production, consumption, labor and leisure, our project looks to the practice of homemade sourdough bread baking during quarantine to ask questions about the ways in which time becomes tangible and gets re-ordered. Specifically, we focus on homemade sourdough bread baking—a popular activity when time at home felt long and bread at grocery stores was scarce—and examine the ways in which this practice, with its demanding and ritualized schedules, became an outlet for temporal control and non-human care. Through semi-structured interviews with Instagram users who have posted about their homemade sourdough bread baking, we explore how bread-baking has served as a means to structure participants' days when the boundaries between formerly distinct time and space arrangements had seemingly dissolved. Ultimately, we articulate bread baking as a 'time-mending practice,' one that, by allowing individuals to exert control through the external demands of sourdough bread, attempts to fix time when it feels so suddenly torn apart—despite its common external markers remaining unaltered.

Synchronizing multispecies lifetimes: The monkey problem in public health and medicine *Tone Druglitrø, TIK Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture, University of Oslo*

Animals have been given little space and thought in historical accounts of public health, despite the fact that animal bodies and lives are carefully weaved into the health of humans. This paper makes an effort to bring nonhumans into the historization of "public health" with a particular focus on how the relationship between human and animal health and immunities have been responded to and safe-guarded in a global health perspective. In the paper, I focus on a specific issue that emerged in the World Health Organization (WHO) during the 1960s on the 'hazards' of using monkeys in biomedicine. Due to several outbreaks of filoviruses in wild monkeys brought into medical laboratories in this period, the WHO developed technical recommendations for building infrastructures and practices that could ensure the safe trade and distribution of monkeys. My interest lies in exploring how different lifetimes as well as temporal relations between humans and nonhumans, presents and futures, were folded into and modified in this (global) public health response to zoonotic risks. The expansive use of monkeys in medicine is a potent example of how natural histories are interweaved with the history of science and medicine, and the extent to which natural histories are crafted, modified and conditioned in conjunction with scientific developments (cf. Landecker 2015, 21). The 'monkey problem' demonstrates the ways in which the infrastructures that enable biomedicine and public health generate new temporal relations between humans and nature objects and environments.

The proliferation of hybrids and the diversification of temporalities in 18th-century British natural science *Erik Ljungberg*

18th-century Britain saw a great increase in new temporal technologies. Mechanical clocks became integrated into daily life. Printing presses churned out calendars, almanacs, and journals which enabled greater efficacy in organizing time. Armed with new temporal devices, natural scientists aimed to map out the rhythms of nature with greater precision. Among these was the naturalist Gilbert White, who maintained a daily record-keeping practice, tracking the movements of 400 species of plants and animals for 25 years. Through converting natural entities into immutable mobiles, White situated the vast multiplicitous rhythmicity of the natural world within a coordinate system of abstract time. Thus White's efforts can be situated within the larger narrative of the increasing dominance

of homogeneous time. However, in this paper I want to reverse the argument and show how 18th-century natural science in Britain, through its employment of emergent temporal technologies, contributed to a proliferation of new forms of time. By drawing on Latour's *We Have Never Been Modern* and using Gilbert White as a case study, I aim to demonstrate how British naturalists were engaged in a Janus-faced project, which on the one hand consisted of creating new hybrids of humans and non-humans, the assemblage of which proliferated new temporalities, and on the other hand, sought to cancel out this hybridization by creating a new form of rhetoric based on the testimony of non-humans, thus creating the appearance of the increasing reign of homogeneous time.

Session Organizer:

Filip Vostal, Institute of Philosophy of the Czech Academy of Sciences

Chair:

Filip Vostal, Institute of Philosophy of the Czech Academy of Sciences

034. Being a Lab, Studying a Lab: Practicing Good Relations in Building Qualitative Research Infrastructures - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Critical STS scholars have exposed "lab life" as a key arena of agentive relations and as sites of more than technical assemblages (Clark and Fujimura 1992, Traweek 1998). Social scientists have also found the form of "a lab" generative for organizing collaborations and essential to gaining institutional recognition and funding. We seek to move beyond the important work of first generation lab studies that demonstrated the political nature of (bench and social) science to place the studying of labs alongside the establishment of qualitative STS labs-- ones that draw on traditional laboratory models yet incorporate alternative frameworks of inclusion and non-extractive epistemologies. Our focus is this dual nature of labs as systems of relations. Extending Roy's (2018) incitement for feminist laboratory methods into the work of qualitative labs, we ask two central questions: what makes a qualitative lab a lab, and what are its methods of good relations? Following Liboiron et al. (2017), how do labs relate to, or materialize in, particular methodologies, ethnographic productions and collaborations?

Participants:

Why Not a Garden? Confronting the Praxis of Qualitative Lab Work Megan Tracy, James Madison University; *Rebecca Howes-Mischel, James Madison University, Department of Sociology and Anthropology*

Prompted by a tweet from a historian of science this year that queried why a lab and not "a workshop (as in the Renaissance) or even a garden" (Yoon 2021) in the social science framing of sustained collaborations and distributed labor, we consider what makes a lab "a lab" and not something else. We approach this from the dual standpoint of the early stages of co-assembling a qualitative research lab and from our joint research project tracking the movement of ideas and materiality across things called labs (in universities and venture-backed capital projects). In both our praxis and our research, we encounter questions of relations, ethics, and institutional considerations. Studying established and dense collaborations has had an iterative effect on our own efforts to construct a generous space of collaboration and mentorship that embraces a specifically feminist STS ethos. Such ethos is challenged by the practicalities of working within institutional spaces outside the research infrastructures and resources of a traditional STEM model. In the spaces that we research, we are likewise confronted by disparate disparities, those brought on by the financial and technoscientific realities of institutional work. In response to pressures from our own educational institutions, as well as those we study, how can we grow a garden where people expect a lab?

Coding the RUSTlab: Discussing, Writing And Living An STS

Lab Ryoko Asai, Ruhr-Universität Bochum; Susana Carmona Castillo, Maastricht University; Olga Galanova, Ruhr-Universität Bochum; Raphael Hemme, Ruhr-Universität Bochum; Laura Kocksch, Ruhr University Bochum; Stefan Laser, Siegen University; Julie Sascia Mewes, Ruhr-Universität Bochum; Abigail Nieves Delgado, Wageningen University; Estrid Sørensen, Ruhr University Bochum

Apart from being a space for doing STS research, the RUSTlab (Ruhr University Science and Technology Studies lab) is also a laboratory for experimenting with modes of building caring relations (cf. Mol 2008, Mol et al. 2015, Puig de la Bellacasa 2017) in academia. A core device for driving this experiment is a document we call "lab coding" to emphasise its fluid and thus shape-shifting character (cf. de Laet & Mol 2000). Our presentation reflects critically the ongoing and living nature of this document and how it both embodies academic practice through detailed descriptions and also installs certain governmentality among lab members. The RUSTlab's coding unfolds through three iterative stages: discussing the code, writing code and trying to live with the codes. As such it continuously trains our "art of noticing" (cf. Tsing 2015) and tests our ways of building relations. The coding aims at realising in academic practice values of care, equity, curiosity and critique inscribed into STS scholarship. However, their realisations also provoked tensions between the formalisation and improvisation of relations, between individual and collective accountability and concerns about identity politics and representations, among others. The coding is inspired by CLEAR lab's "Lab Book" (CLEAR 2018; Liboiron & Molloy 2017) and works as a viable alternative to the rather fixed notion of a "code of conduct", focusing on our situations, particularities and limitations. Our reflexive practice contributes to the broader discussion on labs as academic workplaces. Literature Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action Research (CLEAR) (n.a.) Civic Laboratory for Environmental Action Research (CLEAR) 5m Lab Book: a living manual of our values, guidelines, and protocols. Available at <https://civiclaboratory.files.wordpress.com/2017/12/clear-lab-book.pdf>. Liboiron, M. & Molloy, J. (2017). We need to break science out of its ivory tower – here's one way to do so. The Conversation. April 25. Mol, A. (2008). The logic of Care: Health and the problem of patient choice. Routledge. Mol, A., Moser, I., & Pols, J. (Eds.). (2015). Care in practice: On tinkering in clinics, homes and farms (Vol. 8). transcript Verlag. De Laet, M., & Mol, A. (2000). The Zimbabwe bush pump: Mechanics of a fluid technology. *Social studies of science*, 30(2), 225-263 Puig de la Bellacasa, M. (2017). *Matters of Care: Speculative Ethics in More Than Human Worlds*. (Vol. 41). U of Minnesota Press. Tsing, A.L. (2015). *The Mushroom at the End of the World: On the Possibility of Life in Capitalist Ruins*. Princeton University Press.

Creating a Lab For Diverse Students at Predominantly White Undergraduate Institution (PWUI) Sean Bruna, Western Washington University

In 2015 Western Washington University cancelled classes after a white student threatened the life of a Black student on a social media. The following day students began meeting in a professors small cinder block office, as they had been doing for nearly a year, to discuss and unpack what had happened. That group, composed almost entirely of BIPOC, LGBTQ+ and Disabled students, coalesced to form the Medical Anthropology Lab. This paper examines the Medical Anthropology Lab to provide suggestions for creating a social-cultural "lab" at a Predominantly White Undergraduate Institution (PWUI). We begin with the recognition that historically excluded scholars, including the Latinx presenter of this talk, are rarely trained by

R1 institutions on formation and management of research labs for diverse students, let alone at PWUIs. We then discuss and critique models for building “labs” and their intersection with other kinds of institutional goals, including decolonization of academic departments and shifts towards team-based research. We wish to stress that labs for and by diverse scholars are not centered around reproduction of our experiences of discrimination and inequity. Instead, we argue that diverse labs are centered by open and honest discussions about research, which in turn may shed light on our shared experiences of discrimination and inequity. We close with recommendations for historically excluded faculty that wish to start a lab for diverse students at a PWUI, and encourage all to recognize that in a diverse lab, “the whole is greater than the sum of the parts” (Knight, C. et al. 2021).

STS Labs in STEM Spaces: An Undergraduate Perspective
Alexa Osborn Houck; Courtney Forberg, James Madison University

This paper provides an undergraduate perspective on the experiences of STEM students working alongside and partnering with faculty in an STS lab. As undergraduate students in an interdisciplinary applied science program who are members of the STS Futures Lab at James Madison University, our discussion will focus on the ways in which individual participants formulate research questions to pursue throughout their lab experience. In relation to this, we will interrogate how it is decided what an STS related research question is composed of to consider how good relations are enacted along two axes: as undergraduate students working alongside faculty in research, and as STEM students moving into an STS space. Combining auto-ethnographic reflections on our experiences in the lab with interviews from other lab members, we evaluate the experiences of STEM students in the STS lab in comparison to their experiences and research within a technical lab setting. Additionally, and in conjunction with interviews with faculty and administrators in the institution who’ve interfaced with the lab, we consider what makes the STS Futures Lab a ‘lab’ and how it materializes relations within its STEM context. Throughout our analysis, we highlight the emphasis placed on the consideration of different perspectives in research and discussion, promoting increased awareness and inclusion within our research and the lab setting. Finally, will reflect on differences of the lab space as experienced face-to-face through accounts from previous members who entered during non-virtual circumstances, in contrast to our virtual introduction to the lab during the COVID-19 pandemic.

Session Organizer:

Megan Tracy, James Madison University

Chair:

Rebecca Howes-Mischel, James Madison University,
Department of Sociology and Anthropology

Discussant:

Max Liboiron, Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador

035. Cannabis knowledges: research, regulation practices and implications - I: Cultivation, Multispecies relations and knowledges.

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Participants:

Cannabis as Companion Species. *Julyan Levy*

Cannabis as companion species (Haraway 2003) recognises the agency cannabis has in the human story. It is also a declaration of ethics in how humans can develop sustainable relationships with the plant. I want to begin by reporting on my masters dissertation in human geography - a multi species ethnography on the human-

cannabis relationship (HCR) across scale, from the biochemical to the agroecological. In collecting my data I spoke with a diverse set of people involved in a relationship with cannabis. From small scale hemp farmers to individuals self medicating with cannabis oil for a range of conditions. The popularity, commercialisation and general acceptance of the HCR is far outpacing any research into behaviours and values associated to that relationship. Cannabis is at the centre of an industry that is growing exponentially, especially in health and wellbeing sectors. Yet, academia remains on the outside of the production of knowledge around the “beliefs, practices, values, and social processes” (Hinchliffe, Jackson, Wyatt et al 2018:3) of this significant, forward looking culture. I would like to offer my ideas and suggestions of how the field should expand from here and the challenges involved. Haraway, D. 2003. *The Companion Species Manifesto: Dogs, People, and Significant Others*. Chicago. Prickly Paradigm. Hinchliffe, S; Jackson, M; Wyatt, K; et al. 2018. *Healthy publics: Enabling cultures and environments for health*. Palgrave Communications, 4, (57)

Notes From The Farm: Growing Legal in Humboldt County
Alex Rewegan, MIT

This presentation features a fieldwork report from rural Humboldt County, California, USA where I am conducting ethnographic fieldwork on a legal cannabis farm. It will explore the experiences and perspectives of farmers who are working to successfully operate a legal and sustainable cannabis business. In particular, I will focus on how various farming policies and regulatory requirements are affecting their 2021 agricultural season, especially the practical, affective, and technological relations the farmers develop with their plants and the environment. My analysis will include an exploration of how farmers in the region interact, negotiate, and collaborate with scientists, neighboring farms, and government agencies in developing and experimenting with sustainable and ‘regenerative’ outdoor cannabis policies and practices. Depending on internet access and panel scheduling, the presentation may feature a live call-in from the farm, or will otherwise include a video presentation that features clips, photos, and interviews from the farm site. This fieldwork is part of a multi-sited study of North America’s patchwork landscape of socio-legal cannabis contexts, aimed at understanding how ideas and practices relating to social equity and sustainability are affecting processes of legalization, commercialization, and medicalization.

Session Organizers:

Victor Luiz Alves Mourao, Federal University of Viçosa (UFV-
Brazil)

Paulo Fraga, Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora

Chair:

Daniela Leandro Rezende, Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto

Discussant:

Sandra Lucia Goulart, Faculdade Cásper Líbero - Brazil

036. Centering Public Healthcare II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Though healthcare provides fundamental conditions of (im)possibility for life in the places we research, the workings of public (socialized, employment-based, welfare state) healthcare often remain both allusive and elusive in the studies of science, technology, and medicine (STM). While conceiving of healthcare provision, access, and policy as underlying analyses of biomedical knowledge production, patient-doctor relationships, and illness subjectivities, we seldom explore in depth the co-constitutive forces of the knowledges, practices, and technologies involved in producing, operating, maintaining, and transforming public healthcare. Healthcare structures index particular histories, ethics, and ideologies. They represent a foundational politics of life baked into institutions, pre-structuring care relationships, and organizing social life and membership.

They can be a source of stability, solidarity, and social prosperity, much as they generate gaps and uncertainties, strategic ignorances and bureaucracies of exclusion. We invite fellow STM scholars to help us develop better vocabulary, methods, and theories for understanding and analyzing practices of administering and the administration of public healthcare.

Participants:

IVF in France: The Role of Public Healthcare in Stratified Biomedicalization *Nicola J Marks, University of Wollongong*

IVF and contemporary assisted reproductive practices are paradigmatic examples of what Adele Clarke and colleagues have called biomedicalization: they center around technoscience, are tightly imbricated with corporations and private funding, and they enable new techno-identities and flows of knowledge. In our uneven world, their use is also highly stratified whereby poorer, darker bodies, often from the global South, tend to provide reproductive materials or opportunities for richer whiter bodies from the Global North. However, the stratified biomedicalization of IVF looks very different in different times and places. Here I examine IVF in France, both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic. I find that stratification lines are different there to places such as the U.S. In particular, the provision of reproductive services through public healthcare institutions and the welfare state mean that individual financial means are less important than the normative practices and discourses of these institutions. This becomes more pronounced as the pandemic closes down opportunities for cross border reproductive travel. This paper draws on an analysis of discourses produced by key public healthcare institutions, legislative bodies and commentators. It contributes to the literature on biomedicalization and stratified reproduction, and brings them in conversation with insights from institutional ethnography, governmentality and bioconstitutionalism. It suggests that a pro-natalist history and ideals of “solidarité” have sedimented into French institutions and legislations. However discourses of inclusion also serve to exclude all those who are not categorized as “medically” infertile.

Public Policy Analysis Of The Centralization Of Medical Data in Belgium *Jean-Baptiste Fanouillère*

Following the launch of public policies aimed at digitalizing the health sector in Belgium (e-health plan 2015-2019), healthcare providers decided, after numerous discussions with the federal government, to entrust the development of healthcare records management software to the private sector, mainly for fear that a Big Brother State would control the activity of doctors. Rapidly, however, many healthcare professionals came to regret this choice, and rather feared the monopoly of a few private actors who imposed their conditions on general practitioners. The company Corilus, in particular, distinguished itself by absorbing many competitors, thus reducing the number of healthcare records management software available on the market from around twenty to a handful. Software licenses became more expensive every year and practitioners increasingly became dependent on specific programming languages that prevented portability and interoperability, trapping patient data in proprietary technical infrastructures that acted as black boxes. In parallel, the Covid-19 pandemic recently shed light on the so far rather discreet success of the various e-health plans, which resulted in an opaque and large scale process of centralization of medical data organized by the State, a process which also happens to violate the GDPR. Regulators (the Belgian Autorité de Protection des Données) are however proving powerless, undermined by conflicts of interest both with other government institutions and with large pharmaceutical companies. In this presentation, we propose to analyze both the public policies and the various technical infrastructures that supported the digitization and centralization of medical data, in order to understand the current state of medical data management in Belgium. To achieve this, we intend on the one hand to carry out

a documentary analysis (texts of laws, discourses, reports of the data protection authorities), and on the other hand to interview a series of stakeholders via semi-structured interviews (heads of data protection authorities, authors of draft laws, IT and privacy experts). We will be guided in our analysis by Science and Technology Studies (STS), as well as by the work of Michel Foucault and Nikolas Rose on surveillance and governmentality, particularly in the field of health and medicine.

The Hospital As Technology: Treating Postabortion Complications In A Public Maternity Hospital In Brazil *Mariana Ramos Pitta Lima, Federal University of Bahia*

In Brazil abortion is prohibited, except in three situations: risk of life for the woman; sexual violence; and anencephaly of the foetus. However, illegal, clandestine abortions are the norm. It is estimated that half or more of the women who clandestinely induce an abortion have complications, every year hundreds of thousands of women are admitted to public hospitals to treat them. This paper analyses data from an ethnographic research conducted in 2018 in a public maternity hospital in Salvador, a city located in the Brazilian Northeast, which involved participant observation and interviews. This extract specifically draws on ethnographic data to illustrate the discussion of two central aspects of the type of organisation of public health services in Brazil. The country has a universal system - the Sistema Único de Saúde - SUS - marked for chronic challenges of lack of public resources. The impact is a strong division between a system symbolically built for the 'poor', and the coexistence of a robust private health sector. We argue that the existence of economic and racial stratification, associated with gender stereotypes, where post-abortion care takes place in the "maternity", shapes ways of conceptualising patients, while at the same time being shaped in a situated way in this particular context of organisation of the Brazilian health system. In this sense, this paper argues that technologies - and here we mainly emphasize the public hospital itself as a technology - enacts social relations between professionals-technologies-women - in the daily practice of the hospital.

Which 'Public' in Public Health?: LGBTQ+ Black and Latinx Mobilization in the US During the COVID-19 Pandemic *Nolan Kline, Rollins College*

During the COVID-19 pandemic, the United States (US) operated a patchwork response of varying closures and restrictions that depended on individual states. At the federal level, efforts to address COVID-19 risk focused primarily on elderly populations and largely ignored the disproportionately high risk of COVID-19 exposure among Black, Latinx, and lesbian, gay, bisexual, transgender and otherwise queer-identifying (LGBTQ+) populations. These groups have elevated risk of COVID-19 exposure due to social, political, and economic vulnerabilities that structure poor health. In this paper, I describe how a grassroots racial, sexual, and gender justice organization responded to state failings in meeting the needs of LGBTQ+ Black and Latinx populations during the COVID-19 pandemic. Drawing from ongoing ethnographic fieldwork in Orlando, Florida, that began in 2016 following the Pulse shooting, I describe how a social justice organization advanced a notion of intersectional belonging in response to the absence of health and social services during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, I show how one organization, the Contigo Fund, created an LGBTQ+ COVID-19 relief effort that provided financial assistance to Black and Latinx LGBTQ+ populations when the state of Florida failed to marshal resources for its most marginalized communities. The state's failure is just one of many ways the state has historically refused to meet the needs of populations with intersecting queer and racial minority identities, reproducing longstanding health and social inequities. Overall, I argue that the Contigo Fund's response demonstrates how grassroots mobilization can challenge the necropolitics of state-sponsored neglect and advance health equity.

Session Organizers:

Shoshana Deutsh, Cornell University

Lisa Lehner, Cornell University

037. Citizen Science as Method - III

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Participants:

Advancing Inclusive Engineering Practice Towards the Development of a Model for True Community Driven Research *Jennifer S Carrera*, Michigan State University; *Kent Key*, Michigan State University; *Laura Sullivan*, Kettering University; *Sarah Bailey*, All Faith and Health Alliance; *Cynthia Watkins*, Well Church International Ministries; *Melissa Mays*, Water You Fighting For; *Ronnie Wiggins*, HQLM Vision Center

Environmental justice problems are not simply problems of differential exposure of marginalized communities to specific contaminants but contingent spaces where social determinants of health interact with environmental hazards, political-economic systems, and dynamics of power within a community that increase or decrease residents' willingness or ability to respond in ways that reduce their risks of exposure and harm. While engineering disciplines, particularly environmental engineering, aim to address the environmental and health problems of low-income communities, engineering elevates an expert model and disincentivizes mechanisms that would allow for community engagement by engineering scholars and students. Engineering and STEM fields offer important research resources and innovations needed by marginalized communities but without a mechanism to address power inequities and trust building, these disciplines favor colonial and extractive interventions that may cause more harm than good. Building on a three-year (2018-2021) NIH funded community based participatory research project in Flint, Michigan which focused on developing low-cost technologies to support environmental monitoring and sharing of environmental data amongst Flint residents, our project proposes a mechanism for building an infrastructure inclusive of engineers that will lead to reflexive learning by engineers, community-based cultural education about racialized harm, and trust building with community members to support long-term engagement by academic engineers in community driven research that fosters redress for environmental injustices among marginalized communities.

"Be a Gas Leak Detective": Evaluating a Do-It-Yourself Guide for Finding Urban Gas Leaks *Sarah Lerman-Sinkoff*, Clark University

Buried beneath our homes and workplaces, pipelines transport an invisible threat: flammable natural gas. Country-wide approximately city gas pipes emit 0.69 teragrams of natural gas from ~630,000 leaks each year (Weller et al., 2020). In Boston, ~2.7% of gas brought into the city is wasted in transmission, distribution, and leaks in homes and businesses (McKain et al., 2015). The cost of this \$90 million dollars of lost methane is passed down directly to ratepayers, affecting those with the least ability to pay most intensely. Despite the profound impact that natural gas infrastructure has on residents' lives, significant socio-technical and informational barriers limit residents' ability to intervene in these systems and hold utilities accountable. This research explores the advocacy potential of "Be a Gas Leak Detective", a family-friendly, distance-learning curriculum for finding gas leaks in the urban environment. Developed collaboratively by the climate justice group Mothers Out Front--Worcester and a team of researchers from four academic institutions, "Be a Gas Leak Detective" teaches parents and kids to identify gas injuries to trees and to interpret utility street markings, and discusses the racial and economic justice dimensions of this issue. Building on Fortun & Fortun's (2005)

conception of Civic Science as one that questions the state of things; it does not simply serve the state, this study analyzes what participants learn from engaging in community-lead gas leak walks, and how engaging in these public, performative events shapes users' advocacy towards energy justice.

Cyberinfrastructure For Citizen Science: Converging Practices Through Platforms *Sarika Sharma*, Syracuse University; *Edward Millar*, X University / Ryerson University

Cyberinfrastructure (CI) platforms interoperate citizen science, increasing the scale, centralization, and portability of citizen science data. We argue that these platforms operate as a convergence mechanism for citizen science and frame citizen science as a situated practice that can be augmented if brought in relation to other citizen science projects. Based on a discourse analysis of mission statements and other primary and secondary texts gathered through an analysis of citizen science project aggregators and clearinghouses, we propose a research agenda and framework for theorizing citizen science data sharing platforms as cyberinfrastructure. CI provides converging technologies like APIs that aggregate datasets, gateways to link to other citizen science projects, platforms, portals, integrations and apps design consultancy, and data management and visualization. CI operates as a boundary object providing translation between multiple actors that can include data analysts, data providers, project facilitators, and volunteers. Missions are framed as facilitating data sharing and stewardship, adding rigor into citizen science, supporting the needs of citizen science projects, and improving data portability via standardization, integration, and accessibility.

Re-Envisioning Protocols for Biomedical Citizen Science: The NIH, Self-Empowerment, and Fraught Reciprocity *Jiemini Tina Wei*, Harvard University

In 2015, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) organized a workshop with its employees, outside researchers, patient advocacy groups, and community health organizations to address "Ethical, Legal and Social Implications of Citizen Science," a research approach in which the public actively engages in science as partner or collaborator. Grappling with the myriad implications of citizen science as it moved from its canonical domains of environmental and physical sciences to the biomedical arena, this workshop was curated into a public multi-media digital repository—complete with agendas, video recordings, slides, and compiled tweets. In this presentation, I read this collection of media texts as a digital archive, interpreting it in the context of contemporary biohacking trends and the history of do-it-yourself (DIY) medicine movements. The secondary literature on citizen science's challenge to biomedicine has primarily focused on perspectives of patients, regulatory agencies, and consumer markets. In contrast, this media archive illuminated citizen science's ethical issues from a federally-funded research perspective, focusing on this movement's challenge to biomedical research protocol. Contributing to STS scholarship on self-experimentation, biomedical data-ownership, and scientific method, I argue that this digital repository captured the major complications and conflicts-of-interest embedded in biomedical citizen science. Melding scientific public-participation with self-experimentation, biomedical citizen science posed a fundamental confrontation to traditional biomedical paradigms of double-blind clinical trials. This conflict ultimately centers around the "self," whose incorporation into research is fraught for conventional biomedical research but demanded by biohacking and DIY practitioners.

Session Organizer:

Yasuhito Abe, Komazawa University

Chair:

Jennifer Gabrys, University of Cambridge

038. New Wars on Science II - Public Contestations of Science

9:40 to 11:10 am
4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Participants:

‘Realism’ against Science: Discourse and Argumentation
Analysis of the Association of Climato-Realists *Renaud Hourcade, CNRS - Arènes; Albin Wagener, Université Rennes 2 /INALCO*

Since the advent of a broad consensus on anthropogenic global warming, climatosceptic circles have renewed their strategy in order to spread their ideas. While traditional media have closed down to their theses since the 2010’s (Schmid-Petri et al 2017), climatosceptics have been actively using the devices allowed by the web 2.0 (Gervais 2007), particularly its discursive (Herring 2013) and social (Postigo 2011) possibilities, in order to keep on reaching their audience (Sharman 2014). However, changes brought to their rhetorical techniques to adapt to the new context of scientific and political consensus also call for attention. In France, the “association of climato-realists” , created in 2016, advocates a position of reasonable doubt regarding climate change. Realism is valued as a crucial component of any scientific approach. It is opposed to ‘réchauffisme’ (or ‘warmingism’), which, to them, represents an ideology which wrongly associates global warming (relativized in its causes and effects but no longer denied) with a sense of urgency and bold action (a reaction they call ‘alarmism’). By presenting themselves as reasonable scientists who base their reasoning on scientific principles only, while also staying independent from any political or economic influence, “climato-realists” can act out as a sensible minority oppressed by hegemonic ideological thinking. This paper will study their rhetoric through an analysis of a corpus of web pages and other written and oral productions disseminated by this association. It will be based on a systemic theory of discourse analysis (Wagener 2019) that crosses a lexicometric exploration of the corpus data, while highlighting the argumentative and semantic strategies of the official productions of climato-realists.

“We Will Multiply the Fires of Resistance”: the Catalysts of Dissent and Their Relationship with Refused Scientific Knowledge Groups During the Italian Pandemic Crisis
Simone Tosoni, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore; Paolo Bory; Paolo Giardullo, Università degli Studi di Padova; Valentina Turrini, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore

Recent studies have acknowledged in science-related populism a specific configuration of opposition to institutional science. Mede and Schafer (2020) describe science-related populism as a form of antagonism between ordinary people and allegedly unvirtuous academic and scientific elites. This narrative supports the adoption of an alternative epistemology where true knowledge stems from the first-hand experience of common people. Concomitantly, science-related populism often includes among its “‘post-truth’ repertoires of contesting epistemic authorities” (Ylä-Anttila 2018), the selection of alternative epistemic authorities. Drawing on a 1 year digital ethnography (December 2019 – November 2020), we aim to contribute to the current debate on this emerging form of populism from a twofold perspective. First we describe the role and the relevance - triggered by the pandemic crisis (Lasco and Curato 2019) - of an understudied figure in the diffusion of science-related populism that we named “catalyst of dissent” (CoD). CoDs are public influencers (politicians or media professional) gaining the status of a reference point within a vast and heterogeneous media-ecosystem of resistance to mainstream science. Second, we will shed light on how some key resources produced, detained and disseminated by the CoDs have been appropriated by 3 Italian online Refused Scientific Knowledge Groups (RSKGs) leading to different outcomes at organizational and narrative level within these groups, and more specifically: to a populist turn in one of them (the no 5G scene); to determinate an internal division in

others (the no vax scene); and to foster the role and epistemic authority in still others (5 biological laws groups).

Processed Meat, Nitrite Additives and the Making of Ignorance
Jérôme Santolini, CEA; Marion Desquilbet, Toulouse School of Economics, INRAE, University of Toulouse Capitole, Toulouse, France

Among the different forms of “new wars of science”, we will focus on parascientific institutions such as hybrid entities without scientific production per se and with few active/professional scientists. As an illustration, we will consider the involvement of the French Academy of Agriculture on the issue of the health impact of processed meats. A scientific consensus has emerged over the years on the carcinogenicity of nitrite-based meat curing processes . It has recently become a political issue in France with a series of legislative proposals aimed at reducing the use of nitrite additives, which in turn have generated numerous disinformation initiatives. In this context, the Academy of Agriculture published an opinion considering that the risk of cancer linked to the use of nitrite salts in meat processing was not scientifically established. We will analyse in detail the various nuances and forms of (dis)information in this opinion, the questions raised by its scientific content and its failure to comply with the ethical principles of health expertise as defined in French law. While this opinion has no institutional legitimacy and has major scientific flaws, it has been publicised and considered as a reliable scientific expertise, and its scientific authority has been used by private and public stakeholders to question the scientific consensus on the health effects of nitrite additives. We will examine the public status of such a report, its impact on the public representation of scientific knowledge and authority, and how it has been shaped and exploited for political agendas.

Session Organizers:

Henri Boullier, French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)

Baptiste Kotras, INRAE, LISIS

039. Environ|Mental Urbanities: Problematizing ‘the Mental’ and ‘the Urban’ in Ethnographic Inquiry – II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

In ethnographic inquiries of urban atmospheres, biosocial relations and bodies as practiced, social science scholars situate subjective, embodied experiences in between organisms and environments (Mol 2002, Blackman 2008, Ingold/Palsson 2013, Blok/Farias 2016, Meloni et al. 2018; Seeberg et al. 2020). In doing so, they emphasize how bodily processes are permeated by environmental conditions. However, the adequacy of these approaches for the concomitant embodiment and ecological relationality of ‘mental’ experiences has hardly been addressed directly (among the exceptions are Fitzgerald et al. 2016 and Winz 2018). Relatively few ethnographic research projects attend to the mutual constitution of ‘the mental’ and ‘the environmental’ (Amin/Richaud 2020; Bister et al. 2016). In this panel, we seek to fill this research gap through empirically grounded ethnographic inquiries into ‘mental phenomena’ as part of ‘urban’ life. Our discussion embraces the following conceptual and methodological challenges: How can we grasp elusive aspects of experiences in and of the city as dynamic co-constitutive relations between material environments, cultural practices, subjective experiences, and urban infrastructures? What concepts, methods, and research designs are suitable for combining experience-based approaches (Söderström et al. 2016) with an inquiry in ecologies of expertise (Beck 2015) that shape the urban fabric? What is left of ‘the mental’ if we problematize it ‘environmentally’? How does our research affect how we conceptualize ‘the urban’? Finally, how could our studies inform the design of cities and the crafting of urban cohabitation (Bates et al. 2017)?

Participants:

Feeling Like A City? On Mental Health and Urban Living
Rasmus Birk, Aalborg University

Since the early 20th century it has been argued that living in a city can cause mental health problems. Indeed, there is a long tradition within sociology and geography for thinking about the city as problematic for people's mental health. But questions remain over what, exactly, the relation between mental health and urban life is. In the epidemiological literature exploring this relationship, a plethora of different 'exposures' such as discrimination, pollution, poverty, stress or a lack of green space, are thus amongst the different explanations for why urban life relates so strongly to the development of mental ill health. In this presentation, I will draw on empirical materials from a qualitative study on anxiety and depression in South East London to explore the relationships between urban life, mental health, and feeling. Amongst my arguments will be that our contemporary cultures of expertise and knowledge – especially the 'psy-complex' – are significant elements in how people understand and express their own forms of distress. This troubles the dominant theoretical paradigms in STS, which today are focused on environments and embodiment, and much more rarely engage with human beings as not just embodied, but also as creatures which actively engage in the production of their own circumstances. In short, this presentation will explore urban mental health by focusing on the fraught relationship between feeling and thought, and our contemporary psychological cultures of expertise.

BioEcologies of Encountering: Understanding more-than-social urban cohabitation *Patrick Bieler, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*

What anthropologist Anna Lowenhaupt Tsing (2015, 27) beautifully states to understand how the capitalist ruination of the world has come to be a condition of fungi as multi-species lifeforms, is also a productive lens for inquiry into the co-constitutive relations of mental health and urban environments: "We are contaminated by our encounters; they change who we are as we make way for others. As contamination changes world-making projects, mutual worlds – and new directions – may emerge." (Tsing 2015, 27) In anthropology, the notion of the encounter has traditionally been used to account for the emergence of entanglements between historically and geographically divided social groups in and through colonial practice (Faier/Rolfe 2014). Inspired by ecological thinking (Ingold 2011) I will claim that encounters do constitute a 'contact zone' (Pratt 1992) in which not only cultural but also bodily boundaries are being transcended. Drawing on ethnographic go-alongs with mental health care clients in Berlin, Germany, and relating and contrasting them to psychiatric research that points out causal links between urban living and mental health (Abbott 2012), I will introduce the encounter as an analytic to simultaneously analyze how urban environments are constituted and 'get under the skin' (Galea/Link 2011). By focusing on encounters – more precisely: socio-material processes of encountering – the causality of focusing on the effects of place (neighborhoods) on health as well as a neat separation between the biological and the social can be problematized. This allows to reflect on a more dynamic and more-than-social conceptualization of urban cohabitation (cf. Sampson 2012).

Urbanicity, Sensory Experiences and Mental Health *Josiane Carine Tantchou, Cnrs*

Today >50% of the world's population lives in cities. It is expected that by 2050, this figure will increase to 70%. While living in cities has benefits, like more access to better health care, employment and education, it also leads to increase exposure to risk factors originating from urban social or physical environment (e.g. poverty, traffic noise, pollution), contributing to increased stress and negative mental health outcomes (Lundberg, Cantor-Graae et al. 2009, Golembiewski 2016, Crossley, Allende et al. 2018, Alberto Costa e Silva and Steffen 2019). This is supported by empirical studies in psychology and urban design highlighting that the environment has an epi-and eco-phenomenal impact on mental and physical health. Human

being reacts to inadequate architecture with neuroses (54). Thus, the urban environment/design can have disastrous effect on mental health (Golembiewski 2016). My submission will present the results of an ethnographic research aiming at understanding the links that people diagnosed with a mental disease establish between the materiality and "ambiances" of their environment and their mental health, on the one hand. Collect data related to their sensory experiences (acoustic and olfactory), to comprehend the links they establish between the "noises" and "smells" of their cities and mental health. I expect to capture the matrix of links they establish between their environment and mental health to inform design practices.

Pedagogic atmospheres: Learning to be affected by neurodiverse spatial practices *Tomás Criado, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin; Micol Rispoli, Università degli Studi di Napoli Federico II*

"What would architectural practice look like if rethought from the ecological appreciation of the daily spatial practices of its clients, users and co-designers?" That was the question with which both authors – anthropologist and architect, respectively – engaged in an auto-pedagogical experiment since late 2019, drawing inspiration from cross-fertilising projects in ecological thought and practice that have recently been emerging at the crossroads of design disciplines and STS to rethink the pedagogy of architecture. Indeed, in the last years an experimental agenda has unfolded searching to connect STS approaches to 'technical democracy' and 'assemblage' or 'ecological thought' with the spatial practices of architecture. This agenda has inspired so far relevant conceptual and practical explorations in design studio projects in a web of practitioners at the schools of Architecture in Alicante and Munich: attempting to relearn spatial concepts and practices from conventionally neglected human and nonhuman actors and, more specifically, form their ecological ways of living. Our contribution will describe ethno-graphically our explorations in learning to be affected by neurodiverse spatial practice, addressing its impact not only on (i) the processes, materials, and devices of design practice, but also on (ii) the conventional ocular-centric and volumetric visual culture of architecture. We will show our speculative and provisional results derived from creating both a series of situations to feel concerned with the ecologies and embodied knowledge of neurodiverse people, as well as a series of architectural devices to relearn what a multisensory architecture could be if constructed from the atmospheric spatial practices of neurodiversity.

Session Organizers:

Patrick Bieler, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin
Tomás Criado, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

Chair:

Milena Bister

040. Domesticating Pandemic Troubles: Modelling Covid-19 in an Uncertain World II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Modelling, a scientific practice once reserved for mathematicians, epidemiologists, ecologists and economists, has assumed sudden authority in the covid-19 pandemic. The commanding presence of models in global policy has prompted questions about evidence, reliability and trust. Predictions and forecasting, grounded in formalised assumptions, have shifted the landscape of acceptable evidence in global public health. Moreover, modelling became popular: scores of armchair epidemiologists shared their newfound wisdom, the R-number and "exponential growth" became household terminology, while hashtags like #flattenthecurve entangled "science into social practices, calculations into materialisations, abstracts into affects." (Rhodes et al 2020) In this panel, we will survey how pandemic modelling made relations since early 2020. We will reflect on the unprecedented ways in which pandemic modelling engaged with unequal and uncertain worlds. We encourage two kinds of contributions: 1)

papers which consider the impact of pandemic modelling on knowledge production, policymaking and social relations in pandemic times. Such papers might ask what models do and how they perform as evidence and how modelling has shifted, accelerated or reconfigured persisting challenges of inequality, racism and colonialism. Authors might pay attention to local, regional or national frames of reference. 2) Papers, which investigate the making of relations within models and scrutinize how practices of modelling enfold social, geographical, ecological and microbiological assumptions when forecasting the pandemic world. We invite papers focusing particularly beyond Europe and North America to ask what constitutes good relations within modelling practices, and how we might reconcile these with an ethics of care, responsibility and solidarity.

Participants:

Absence as Presence: decomposing absence of disease in data and modelling practices *Francis Lee, Chalmers University of Technology*

This paper seeks to highlight absence as a crucial category to pay attention to in critical analyses of modelling, algorithms, and data. Absence is the taken for granted category that bounds and delimits the real matter of concern. Absence is the thing that we are not after. That which we take no interest in. That which is discarded. At the edge of the data that matters. As such, absence is often left unscrutinized—but absence is just as precariously enacted and composed as presence. This paper analyzes how a set of actors construct absence in their work to predict disease. Based on fieldwork at the European Centre for Disease Control and Prevention, the paper analyzes how the seemingly straightforward absence of disease breaks down into a multitude: absence of data, absence of cases, absence of modelled risk, as well as simulated “pseudo absence.” In practice, the simple category of “no disease” turns out to contain many layers. This case points to the analytical and empirical importance of not just paying attention to those things that are made present in the world, the matters of concern, or the facts of the matter—but also to the making of absences, nothings, and blank spaces. How do we analyze that which bounds the matters of concern, and turn our eyes to the absence that surrounds it?

Anticipating Uncertain Futures: Pandemic Modelling And Healthcare Governance Of COVID-19 *Syb Kuijper, Erasmus School of Health Policy & Management; Jenske Bal, Erasmus University Rotterdam; Sabrina Huizenga, Erasmus University Rotterdam; Bert de Graaff, Erasmus University Rotterdam; Roland Bal, Erasmus University Rotterdam*

In this study, we analyse the different ways in which Dutch hospitals and national and regional networks of acute care have responded to uncertainty in relation to the Covid-19 pandemic, as it unfolded in the Netherlands. Mediated by scenarios, models, projections and prognoses, these responses result in different ways of anticipating the virus and illuminate different relationships with uncertainty, temporal logics and (imagined) futurity. We scrutinize how models are established and lived as anticipated potentials (Rhodes & Lancaster, 2020), influencing action and policy in the now (Anderson, 2020), actualised in social practices and regional and national policies. By considering the performative effects of models we analyse how different ways of anticipation are mediated and how they co-constitute healthcare governance, with important consequences for healthcare delivery. We show the political and normative variability of modelling practices and the ways in which regional healthcare governance-actors have responded during the different ‘waves’ of the Covid-19 pandemic, suggesting different ways in which the future is enacted. The paper is based on a fully embedded ethnographic study of the organisation and decision-making within the COVID-19 crisis in the Netherlands, starting March 2020 and proceeding to this day. The authors conducted non-participatory observations (+/- 600 hours) and semi-structured interviews (+/- 60) within four hospitals and the national and regional executive bodies responsible for the spread

of COVID-19 patients. This layered case allows us to show what models do and how they are ‘made to matter’ within Dutch healthcare during the COVID-19 pandemic.

COVID-19 modelling as a collective appropriation of scientific practices and evidence: the case of Ecuador *Sofia Carpio, Kaleidos Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*

The onset of the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020 posed a number of challenges to scientists, health officials, policy makers, institutions and governments around the globe and called for the urgent generation of knowledge concerning the new threat (SARS-CoV-2). Most importantly, it called for the translation of said knowledge into policies, protocols and strategies to navigate uncertainty at an unprecedented speed and scale. Epidemiologists and data analysts turned their efforts to building their own versions of susceptible-infected-recovered (SIR) models and case projections. This trend was mirrored in countries in the Global South as well. In Ecuador, these efforts were compounded by difficulties in data production and availability, prompting social organizations to establish efforts to monitor available public data. The aim of this article is twofold. First, we seek to document efforts by academics, data analysts and civil society in Ecuador to model the pandemic and offer projections to the public. Then, we examine how they engaged in practices of interpreting and (in the case of those outside epidemiology) appropriating knowledge from outside their area of expertise, and the lessons from these efforts. Did these works succeed in producing knowledge to design better responses to the pandemic? More importantly, what other goals do these exercises fulfill in the interpretation and appropriation of scientific findings and discourses produced abroad and in other contexts? How do these efforts contribute to expanding the “model society” (Rhodes, 2020) and what does this experience reveal about modelling as a scientific practice?

Session Organizer:

Kari Lancaster, University of New South Wales, Sydney

041. Evidence and perspectives of social innovation - II: Technology & Social Change

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

In recent decades, several international organizations such as the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development, the European Commission and the World Economic Forum have stated that nation’s progress must be understood in a broader set of ideas, including not just technological innovation but also social innovation (SI). Although the term has been used in sociological discourses and within other disciplines since the late 19th century, SI has gained attention in academia and political discourses since the beginning of the 21st century. There are several conceptions about SI; the term is used differently across diverse disciplines. Conceptions go around “doing something good within or for society”, “changing social practices and/or structure”, or “contributing to rural and community development”. Likewise, there is an exponential growth of academic literature dealing with SI, so that an increase of success experiences is presumed. Like this, it is also presumed that SI is becoming the most convenient innovation paradigm to face the social, economic, political and environmental challenges of the 21st century. In response to this outlook, through this open panel we invite STS scholars to join a discussion on SI that presents empirical research results, showing evidence of specific SI processes, as well as perspectives that allow feedback on emerging practices, experiences and application. In the second session of the panel we will discuss different cases that involve technology used in social transformation (in positive and negative aspects), as well as technology with sustainable purposes and designed to be beneficial for society.

Participants:

Blockchain Utopias and Societal Transformation Daniel Kim, University of California, Berkeley; Sreela Sarkar, Santa Clara University

History has shown that the introduction of new communication

and information technologies is routinely accompanied by a cloud of uncritical and deterministic rhetoric, including rapturous celebration and prophecies of transformative changes. Employing terms like 'technological sublime,' 'techno utopianism,' and 'techno optimism,' scholars have turned to the discursive formations that enable and disable vast commitments by societies in search of solutions to a wide range of societal problems. In this spirit, this paper examines the techno-utopian rhetorics around the relatively new technology known as 'blockchain.' While the impacts of blockchain within finance have become familiar thanks to sensationalistic news coverage about cryptocurrencies, there is an increasing number of "social innovation" projects featuring blockchain presented as solutions to deep-rooted problems through an emphasis on concepts like openness, decentralization, security, participation, and scalability. Across thousands of blockchain-powered projects, corporations and governments promise that blockchain will solve problems spanning diverse domains such as elections, education, immigration, healthcare, intellectual property, and food supply chains. Drawing on a range of critical perspectives, including feminist and postcolonial theory, we examine the mobilization of blockchain in promised societal transformations based on an analysis of institutional and popular discourses. We demonstrate that the topology of hopes and promises attached to emerging blockchain-integrated technologies conceal asymmetrical power relations based on technocratic "expertise" and deep-rooted structural inequities.

Does sustainability matter for makerspaces? The perceptions and practices of the French fablabs. *Beyza Coskun, Middle East Technical University Science and Technology Policy Studies; Arsev Umur Aydinoglu, Middle East Technical University; CEDRIC GOSSART, Institut Mines-Télécom Business School; Müge Özman, Institut Mines-Télécom Business School*

By means of personal fabrication, and the inherent community spirit, fablabs have great potential for; localization of production, reducing digital divide, ensuring social integration and develop sustainable urban projects as a building block of social innovation. Furthermore, being a manifestation of grassroots innovations movements, it is expected from the fablabs to seek alternative sustainable solutions. This research focuses on fablabs located in France. How do French fablabs perceive social innovation and sustainability? How do they integrate Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) in their agendas? How can their partners help them contribute to SDGs? What are the causalities behind the different perceptions and contributions for sustainability, their stakeholders, their dominant organizational identity, their principles, or their community? Which organisational practices do they put in place to contribute to SDGs? To answer these questions, an online survey was distributed to French fablabs, and in-depth interviews were carried out on site. The UN SDG framework was used to analyse their sustainability contributions. Preliminary findings include: (1) French fablabs are aware of SDGs; (2) Most contribute to SDG12 "Responsible Consumption and Production"; (3) Most are non-profit organizations; (4) Most are very sensitive to sustainability issues (e.g. regarding repair, recycle and re-use processes), which makes them key contributors to SDGs. There are very few studies about fablabs and their relationship with social innovation and sustainability in the scientific literature. This is the first research study on the French Fablabs, to understand their contribution to SDGs which would lead further research in developing countries on this subject.

Role of Scientific Institutes in the Development of Molecular Diagnostic Innovation System in India: An Approach Towards Social Innovation *Nidhi Singh, Jawaharlal Nehru University*

The present study is an attempt to examine the System building

activities of Indian Scientific Institutes in the development of Molecular Diagnostic (MDs) Innovation System. Scientific Institutes are the precursor of any technological development with their capabilities in the generation of new ideas. MDs is an advanced and accurate diagnostic technology that has considerable scope to serve the diagnostic needs and requirement of the healthcare system. Study adopted a System framework to analyse the System Building activities of scientific institutes' involved in the constitution of the science base for the development of MDs technology. The system performance was evaluated in terms of Technological Innovation System functions and the systematic challenges and issues are assessed through System failure methodology. The knowledge production for the development of MDs has got significant momentum in last one decade with the development of specialised human resource and establishment of dedicated research institutes. Moreover, the innovative capabilities in terms of attaining need based Technological Innovation System are found to be sub-optimal in terms of meeting the specific diagnostic needs for highly burdened diseases in the country. The system analysis reveals that at present the TIS functions are underperforming because of the absence of well-defined funding mechanism and goal oriented targeted policy regime of the State. Since MDs has transformative effect on the present healthcare diagnostic system, State has to address the system-based challenges and issues for developing a need based social innovation system for MDs in the country.

Social innovation in renewable energy: communities, cooperatives and other grass-root initiatives *Ana Delicado, Instituto de Ciencias Sociais, ULisboa; Monica Truninger, Institute of Social Sciences University of Lisbon; Michela Ghislanzoni, Territoria*

Climate change mitigation and energy transition will no doubt require large scale transformations to be effective: the widespread adoption of renewable energy and energy efficiency practices by industry, utility companies and domestic consumers. However, increasing attention is being paid to the role that social innovation, through distributed, smaller scale initiatives, can have in empowering citizens and meeting their needs and expectations regarding energy sources, services and local participation in an effective and cost-efficient way. Social innovation thus materializes in energy cooperatives, energy communities and microgrids. This presentation will examine four case studies of social innovation in the renewable energy sector in Portugal and Spain. These two countries share some specific characteristics: very favorable conditions for renewable energy production, in particular solar energy; the energy markets are dominated by large incumbents; and the long shadow of authoritarian regimes in the 20th century still stifles political and social participation. It is based on the identification of relevant cases of social innovation regarding renewable energy (novel more sustainable solutions to problems such as community opposition, landscape impacts, underdeveloped RE generation potential), followed by document analysis and interviews with stakeholders (promoters, participants, residents, civil society organizations). We will discuss how these renewable energy initiatives deliver social benefits for communities, fight social exclusion, mobilize citizens and allies, and improve structures of governance, but also the challenges and hurdles they face (bureaucratic regulatory frameworks, lack of government support, competition from market-reliant approaches).

Session Organizer:

José Francisco Romero-Muñoz, Benemérita Universidad Autónoma de Puebla - Dirección de Innovación y Transferencia de Conocimiento

042. Disciplinary Translations in Science and Society - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Recent events worldwide have shown the relevance of interdisciplinary approaches to cope with uncertainty: the current pandemic and sanitary crisis, social and political protests, climate emergency -among many others- prove the need to think—and act—in novel and creative ways. More than disciplines examining phenomena from different standpoints, innovative interdisciplinary approaches need to conceptualize past and emerging problems from assemblages at the interaction of various fields. In this way, effective interdisciplinary studies could contribute to understanding our world from a more complex, dense, and purposeful perspective. At the crossroads of society and science, STS offers a strong potential to trespass traditional knowledge production boundaries. This panel seeks to explore the role of “disciplinary translations” in studying science and societies. Disciplinary translations refer to the transfer of concepts, ideas, frameworks produced in science and applied to understand social dilemmas and vice versa. To mention just a few examples, there have been experiences of applying complex models of physics to understand social networks; chaos theory to study social behaviors in crowds; chemical transformations in matter to analyze historical processes. This panel aims to bring together proposals from different fields exploring this post-disciplinary approach to both science and society. Additionally, the purpose of this panel is to discuss how STS could contribute to shaping both compelling and effective interdisciplinary knowledge production.

Participants:

History of infrastructures in Puerto Edén: using a timeline to achieve interdisciplinary dialogue *Cecilia Ibarra, Universidad de Chile; Romina Pizarro, Escuela de Puerto Edén; Cristian Valenzuela Calderon, Universidad Alberto Hurtado*

In March 2020, our research team embarked on the study of practices of maintenance and repair in remote locations. The project aims at learning from transitions towards more sustainable practices in isolated regions. One of our case studies is the abandoned hydroelectric turbine in Puerto Eden, a village on the Wellington Island in the Chilean Patagonia. The original research strategy consisted of a historical approach combining an institutional perspective, based on secondary sources and government archive, and local perspectives, based on interviews and ethnographic methods. The sanitary crisis made our plans impossible. Hoping to travel later in the year, we advanced on our research using secondary sources and available records of interviews. To cope with the new conditions, we had to find a new approach and trespass our academic boundaries to produce knowledge in a transdisciplinary way, working with the local community. We formed a team with the local school teacher, who integrated the project to the school curricula of the eighteen students. Together we are set to document practices of construction, maintenance and repair of the communal infrastructures of Puerto Edén. We agreed on common objectives and on using a timeline as a tool to translate and integrate our views and to explore ways of producing transdisciplinary knowledge. The first version of the timeline was based on our previous research and it is being transformed by the current research of the students and our own in a dialogic process.

pTA as Policy Innovation in NASA's Asteroid Initiative *Christopher G Torres, Boise State University*

There is a substantial body of published work in the field of STS on the challenges to incorporating pTA in government science and technology decision-making. There has been little work, however, examining how pTA works in the context of U.S. federal government agency science and technology decision-making processes. This paper reports on part of a comparative study of three pTA experiments undertaken by the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA), the Department of Energy, and the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration in partnership with the Expert and Citizen Assessment of Science and Technology (ECAST) network, specifically, on NASA's use of pTA to inform the 2014 Asteroid Initiative. Through a qualitative analysis of interviews conducted

with NASA personnel and ECAST members, and using Kingdon's Multiple Streams Approach from policy studies, I identify several organizational, political, and administrative factors that supported and challenged pTA in NASA mission and program design. This work demonstrates how federal personnel involved in the pTA project acted as “policy entrepreneurs” who facilitated navigating the agency's political pressures and the administrative challenges to deliberative experimentation. Moreover, ECAST collaborations with government agencies to experiment with deliberative public participation in government decision-making show us the messy bureaucratic negotiations between forum organizers and U.S. government agency personnel concerning forum design and the political pressures and administrative challenges agencies face. STS participatory theory and practice can benefit from a more systematic knowledge of what these political pressures and administrative challenges are, and how policy entrepreneurs within U.S. federal government agencies facilitate them.

Reflections on How Dark Matter Could Illuminate History of Science *Barbara Kirsi Silva, Universidad Alberto Hurtado*

The study of dark matter is an ongoing field in astronomy. Dark matter and dark energy sum up approximately 95% of our universe, and still poses questions about its characteristics, dynamics and composition. That means that what we actually know about our universe is barely a 5%: photons and matter we can see. Astronomers currently struggle to find material proof of dark matter's existence. For them to study dark matter, they have to access it through light -that scarce 5% of what we see. If we apply this basic principle to the discipline of history, the structure might be quite similar. Although we do not have percentages, what we know about the past is a scarce proportion, defined by sources, traces people of other times left behind. But the past is more diverse, complex, and has other edges for which we do not have records or specific sources. However, this does not mean that the only past that existed was the one we have sources for. Therefore, we try to access those “dark” portions of our past throughout the sources we do have. This paper proposes studying the history of Dark Matter by using this parallel between disciplines. If we work with this interdisciplinary approach, we can understand the potential of reading and interpreting sources, as doorways to unknown aspects of the past. This perspective allows us to formulate new questions discussing the connections between science and society in the past.

Separated Yet Connected: Prevention of Antimicrobial Resistance in Swedish Veterinary and Human Medicine *Hedvig Gröndal*

Sweden has been successful in lowering the use of antibiotics in human health care as well as in veterinary medicine – today the Swedish consumption of antibiotics in both these areas is among the lowest in Europe. In Swedish official documents the cross-sectional character of Swedish Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) prevention is described as crucial for this success. However, the early reduction of antibiotic use in human health care and veterinary medicine were not parallel in time and appear to have been two separate processes at large, mobilizing different sets of actors and constituting AMR in different ways. In this paper the connections between these processes are investigated. I argue that, on the one hand, their separate character have been key to the reduction of antibiotic use. AMR was produced as a matter relevant to both veterinary medicine and human health care; as a matter of increasing animal welfare and food safety in relation to the former, and as a way of preventing spread of antibiotic resistant bacteria in relation to the latter. On the other hand, I also argue that the connections created between these processes have been crucial for the current privileged status of AMR in Swedish politics and policy. The Swedish case illustrates that coordinated and cross-sectional prevention of a phenomenon, drawing on shared understandings, is not always necessary, but that to some extent, absence of coordination can actually be fruitful. However,

it also shows that separate processes does not exclude productive connections and partial coherence.

Session Organizer:

Barbara Kirsi Silva, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

Chair:

Barbara Kirsi Silva, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

043. How to Read the How-to, Part II: Sounding the Manual

9:40 to 11:10 am

AS 2021 Virtual: 20

Salomé Skvirsky (2020) defines the process genre, or “how-to”-ness, as “the sequentially ordered representations of making or doing something.” Moving beyond the question of replicability in experimentation (e.g., Collins 1985), we take inspiration from Skvirsky to invite submissions that explore aesthetic qualities of the how-to genre in knowledge-making practices. Specifically, we want to extend her analysis to scientific and social-scientific manuals. In thinking about objects like field guides, ethnographic textbooks, ecological surveys, personal research journals, archeological codes and conventions, we ask: what kind of affects, attachments and aesthetic experiences are produced and reproduced in the doing of science and through its representation in manuals? Skvirsky focuses on absorption, but we also invite papers that explore other feelings like boredom, love, anxiety, resentment, awe, etc. How are they enabled by the “how-to” genre of the manual? And how does this genre produce, reproduce, and disrupt relations, good or otherwise, between knowledge producers, objects of study, disciplines, institutions, and places? The manual is also a genre of theory seen in the exemplar of J. L. Austin’s *How to do Things With Words*, Bruno Latour’s *Science in Action: How to Follow Scientists and Engineers through Society* and, to a certain extent, in Kate Brown’s *Manual for Survival*. We therefore invite submissions that interrogate a “how-to” manual as an object of analysis, but also as a mode of STS analysis and theorization, or, better yet, written in the how-to genre itself!

Participants:

Culture as Reification **Kasia Kalina**, *University of Chicago*,
Department of Anthropology

The “accidental” discovery of hydrocarbon deposits in Colombia’s Magdalena Valley by Dutch scientists stranded in the country during World War II led to the rapid, highly improvisational construction of company towns and recruitment of migrant workers, most of whom were in the process of fleeing the paramilitary violence of Andean settlers in majority-black coastal and lowland regions. Managerial staff echoed existing Andean elite anxieties regarding the distinct communist threat posed by the labor militancy of the towns’ black workers as inevitably resulting in the enslavement of white and mestizo elites as vengeance for the history of slavery (Wade). In order to supplement existing repressive labor management tactics, Shell-employed ethnomusicologists were tasked with collecting field recordings and written field guides pertaining to the traditional musics associated with the workers’ regional origins. The resulting ten-volume *Shell Album of Colombian Rhythms series (1957-1966)* and accompanying fieldbooks were distributed as gifts to employees and subsequently came to be frequently sold and consumed outside of in-house employee networks. As is the case with Skvirsky’s examination of the process genre, these albums and fieldbooks—which carried instructions regarding appropriate dance techniques and denotational information regarding each form’s cultural origins—were aimed at the absorption of worker attention. This absorption includes and exceeds the reification of the individual worker’s body-psyche as is the case in Lukács’s examination of the Taylorist assembly line. I argue that this particular process genre entails the reification of history into discrete synchronic objects of culture, and in so doing constitutes the grounds of expanded reproduction of multiple coterminous historicities of unfree labor.

Programming and Meta-Programming in the Electro-Organism: Learning to Play the Human Body as an

Electronic Musical Instrument **Theodore Gordon**, *Baruch College, City University of New York*

In the early 1970s, a new kind electronic musical instrument began to appear in the consumer marketplace: the voltage-controlled synthesizer. Once only available as custom-built systems for academic and government-sponsored electronic music studios, these new instruments miniaturized and systematized disparate types of electronic circuits, ostensibly allowing for the smooth flow of electricity, understood as musical “information,” within a single apparatus. The only problem was that most musicians, untrained in electrical engineering, information theory, or cybernetics, had no idea how to use them. In this paper, I examine Allen Strange’s manual, *Programming and Meta-programming in the Electro-Organism*, written in 1974 to instruct users how to use the Buchla Music Easel. This ostensibly “user-friendly” instrument consisted of two interconnected modules in a stainless-steel suitcase, and was designed by Don Buchla, the first person to produce modular electronic music systems in San Francisco in 1965. By the early 1970s, Buchla’s design philosophy had evolved from early influences of information theory and cybernetics to more the more esoteric para-scientific thought of researchers such as John C. Lilly, whose experiments with cetaceans led him to conceptualize bodies as “biocomputers” and “the mind” as sets of “programming and meta-programming.” Directly citing Lilly’s research, Strange’s manual posits a para-scientific, systems-theoretical paradigm for the performance of electronic music. By likening the human being to an electronic musical instrument, Strange’s manual teaches humans how to use this instrument, cybernetically connected to their mind-body, in a way that promised to expand possibilities for human creativity, sensation, and consciousness.

The role of the kit and assembly manuals in DIY audio scene

Jose Antonio Llorente Sesma

In the world of D.I.Y. amateur audio, kits and assembly instructions allow the culture’s development of building electronic sound instruments and equipment. They are the key element that structures the workshops and activities, establishes technical knowledge and allows economic exchange. Through the ethnographic work carried out around the D.I.Y. audio eurorack scene in Barcelona, my research explores the kits and assembly instructions as artifacts transmitters of technical knowledge, open source hardware ethics and aesthetics of the sound art community. How does a community learn through its technical documents? How important are they in order to build a common experimental culture scene? Do they describe “how to do” things or “how to become” a maker? An audio kit is a heterogeneous set of materials that includes electronic components and PCBs, assembly documents, expressive instructions (Sennet, 2008) and other graphic and media such as stickers, flyers and fanzines. The assembly instructions configure a display of actions that involve the maker’s decision-making and create after its execution a musical instrument for sound experimentation. They are both technical documents and art performance scripts, and I consider this duality being a contribution to the study of STS, in the essence of Art-by-instruction (Cage, 1956) for the development of a technological “happening”.

Session Organizer:

Emma Pask, University of Chicago

Chair:

Boyd Ruamcharoen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

044. Mediation, Probability, and Environmental Risk - III: Resource Extraction and Risk Analysis

9:40 to 11:10 am

AS 2021 Virtual: 21

The mining of precious minerals and other resources has led to environmental destruction, displacements, and threats to human health around the world. In the wake of extractive capitalism and global energy transitions, efforts to manage, represent, and predict environmental risk both contribute to and often conceal the human perceptions and experiences of risk on the ground. Recognizing that extractive frontiers are often incubators for risk assessment methods, this session considers the production and management of risks through probabilistic tools, analysis, and other modes of mediation. Key themes from these papers include modes of thinking about the local and the global together, scalar mediations of risk across communities and geographies, and decolonial perspectives. Together, these contributions put into question both ontological and epistemological conceptualizations of environmental risk adopted by extractive industries, countering existing discourses with an ethical charge to connect technological quantifications of risk to material and lived experiences. The session also considers how science fictional media, including environmental gaming, can foreground discrepancies between the speculative profits of extractive capitalism and affective, cultural imaginaries of risk. This includes an exploration of the black swan event—unpredictable yet catastrophic externalities that escape the operations of probabilistic risk analysis.

Participants:

Managing mining uncertainties: does risk analysis make the world more risky? *Tarık Nejat Dinç*

In his keynote speech in the international Tailings and Mine Waste Conference in 2011, Andy Robertson, the founder of Robertson GeoConsultants Inc. noted regarding mining waste dams that “risk factor has increased by a factor of 20 every 1/3 century”. It appears paradoxical to see a constant increase in the frequency and magnitude of mining waste dam failures with catastrophic environmental and social effects during a period when quantitative risk analysis become more and more an integral part of managing mining safety and uncertainties. Through an analysis of the environmental conflict surrounding the construction of Turkey’s first gold mine at the turn of the century, this paper addresses this paradox by ethnographically uncovering how risk reality is enacted and acted upon through the field of risk analysis built upon probabilistic risk calculus. To this end, it scrutinizes in detail how the probabilistic risk assessment of the waste dam prepared by a world renowned consultancy firm performs risk calculus, circulates risk thresholds, and strategically oscillates between objectivity and subjectivity - an inherent ambiguity in risk analysis. In doing so, I show that: 1) the technical field of risk analysis, rather than being a quantitative endeavor to “grasp actual risks”, is a performative dispositif in the sense of enacting the reality that it claims to describe; 2) such an endeavor necessarily entails incompleteness, which it tries to conceal through a triumvirate governing the field: actual risk, risk perception and communication of risk; 3) such incompleteness in turn results in counter-performativity where the risk reality enacted becomes materially more risky, and ultimately more harmful.

On repopulating scalar discourses: Scaling Risk and Effects with reference to the Lithium Mining in the Atacama Desert *Joshua DiCaglio, Texas A&M*

In 2019, I went to a showing of the film "Anthropocene: The Human Epoch," which showcases many terrifying large-scale human projects including the lithium mining in the Atacama Desert. In the Q&A, a man introduced himself as the representative of the people just displayed in the film. His message: "Please do not destroy our homeland in order to make up for your mistakes." In this moment, the aesthetic yet horrifying scenes portrayed by the film were abruptly repopulated and made present. In this paper, I use the disorientation of this moment to consider the scales at which environmental risk and effects are able to be seen, thinking about discourses and representations that cross scale domains. Just as the demands for energy transition impact the people of

these indigenous communities in the Atacama desert, our discourse on risks displaces the particularities of the human scale even as it connects these human realities to other-scale impacts. This is one essential challenge presented by scale: because scalar discourses and interventions pull us outside of our of the human lifeworld, they have to be in a sense "repopulated" by reconnecting them to this-scale realities. I define a "scalar discourse" as any representation that crosses at least two scale domains. In this way, this representation of lithium mining in the Atacama mirrors the repeated challenges presented by statistics: statistics, in a sense, speak of an object on one scale in terms of another (i.e. your health in relation to the aggregate of humans). Doing so always tempts us to forget or depopulate the very things we're talking about (i.e., your body, the Atacama desert). To counter this problem, we do not just need better images of our effects on other scale, but we also need to resituate these statistics and effects in the properly scalar view.

Playing in Dangerous Waters *Lisa Han, Arizona State University*

In *Other Waters* is a text-based adventure game that posits a mysterious, futuristic narrative set in the extraterrestrial oceans of planet Gliese 677Cc. Like other ocean exploration games such as *Subnautica* or *Abzû*, it challenges players to acquire information about a mysterious wilderness through acts of resource collection, exploration, mapping, and monitoring of physical parameters. However, while suggestions of danger abound, In *Other Waters*' topographic map, text-based narrative, and simple navigation interface refuse the photorealistic visuals, urgency, and speed that typically accompany game mediations of risk. Instead, sonic ambience and a graphical dashboard foreground philosophical questions around how curiosity, empathy, and affect are experienced through more-than-human assemblages of man, machine, and nature. Through textual and historiographic analysis, I examine the ways in which In *Other Waters* incorporates scientific subjectivity, AI technology, and instrumentalist impulses to control nature within an experience of environmental novelty and risk. Moreover, I critique the ways in which acts of extraction, mapping, and cataloguing have taken primacy in Western encounters with environmental uncertainty. These mechanics replicate real world regimes of scientific management and quantification, and reflect how smart technologies are often discursively collapsed into notions of resilience and reassurance in the face of climate change, particularly within contemporary ocean research. I argue that the main affordance of this game is that it first situates players as high-tech corporate scientists, forcing them to slowly arrive at an ecocentric, preservationist ideology that critically questions the very ethics of experimentation, technological determinism, and exploitation that undergird its gameplay.

Session Organizer:

Lisa Han, Arizona State University

Discussant:

Anne Pasek, Trent University

045. Mapping the Conceptual Vocabulary of AI in the Global South - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

The possibilities of leveraging Big Data through AI-based interventions are often poised to flow as innovations emerging from the Global North as the active center to the Global South as the passive periphery. Problematizing these flows, this panel is oriented towards showcasing that the Global South is neither a passive recipient, nor is it the periphery of these innovations. The panel invites submissions that identify new and/or reinterpret old concepts and keywords that underlie the emerging meaning(s) and future(s) of AI in the Global South. The range of conversations on this topic operates on a wide spectrum between optimism of leapfrogging and digital transformation of societies on one end and the pessimism of human suffering caused by new forms of data capitalism and

colonialism on the other. Mapping this spectrum, the members of this panel will not only present their concepts, keywords, research methods, and case studies in understanding the building and consequences of these technologies, but also collaboratively engage with each other in developing a broader conceptual vocabulary of AI in the Global South. The panel asks what stories of AI are told and shared, what unequal and uncertain world(s) do these stories build, what hopes and concerns do they amplify, and what future(s) do they imagine in the Global South. After all, the concepts and keywords to describe the mutual shaping of AI and society have different intellectual trajectories in different parts of the world. Recognizing this difference is the first step towards understanding it.

Participants:

What does Feminist AI mean? A critical survey of the writings on the subject *Sophie Toupin, University of Amsterdam*

This presentation sheds light on the different meanings associated with the broad category of feminist artificial intelligence. I use the term artificial intelligence as a generic concept and I have decided to broaden the meaning of feminism to reflect its contemporary manifestations including its revolutionary (Bhandar & Ziadah, 2020), intersectional (Crenshaw, 1991; Combahee River Collective, 1981), black feminist (hooks, 2000) and decolonial inflections (Verges, 2019). The two signifiers Feminism and AI are thus broad enough to include the practices and thinking that this presentation sets to survey. The terms feminist AI, Intersectional AI, Black AI and decolonial AI have been mobilised lately by academics, activists and practitioners as a response to the bias within the thinking of the category of AI, the discrimination and sexism within the development of applications, and the call to diversify the people engaged in this discipline and practice, among others. In this presentation, I review a number of articles and books written by academics that include the terms feminist artificial intelligence, Black artificial intelligence, Intersectional artificial intelligence and decolonial artificial intelligence. I also include articles written by and practices of activists and techies who use these categories. Methodologically, this presentation is not based on a systematic and exhaustive review of all material published on the subject but rather a critical survey of some writings that shed light on the different understandings of feminist AI as broadly understood.

Inclusive AI? *Seyram Avle, University of Massachusetts Amherst; Till Straube, Goethe University Frankfurt*

Bias in artificial intelligence (AI) systems has been attributed to a lack of diverse training data. A more inclusive data set, so the argument goes, will minimize errors, leading to greater accuracy and therefore less bias. A frequent counterpoint has been that biased AI systems reflect systemic issues from the institutions that build and use them and subsequent calls have been made to ban specific applications such as facial recognition technologies (FRT) in various parts of the world. In this paper, we ask, how do such narratives around AI and FRT move across geographies as the markets for these technologies expand? Specifically, what does inclusivity in AI mean in particular sites, and how does that become enrolled in particular state and market actions that lead to the development and deployment of these technologies. Drawing on discourse analysis of AI and FR technologies (from both domestic and international markets particularly China and the United States) being taken up in parts of Africa, this paper showcases the transmutability of 'inclusivity' within technocentric discourses of progress and futurity.

Raciality of Technoscience: AI Development in Africa *Yousif Hassan, York University*

Historians of science highlighted the shift in understanding "Western science" as universal and global science. For example, scholars show how the conception of the global notion of science is shaped by colonial historical narratives about ourselves and our world. They argue that "the global emergence of the idea of Western science highlighted key questions pertaining to the

relation of the history of science to knowledge traditions across the world and the continuing search for global histories of science". However, the modern notion of the "global" today denotes the interconnectedness of the world through nested structures of capital, trade, race, gender, class, and empire. Objects of science, technology and innovation are placed within other objects of finance and contemporary capitalism. Underpinned by decolonial understanding of technoscience and contemporary Black/African studies perspective, this paper aims at answering the following two main questions: is AI development a global technoscience project? How so? And how should concerns of raciality be approached in the development of AI technology in the Global South? Using case study of the African Master in Machine Intelligence program at the African Institute for Mathematical Sciences, this paper locates narratives of technological innovation in AI development in Africa within their colonial and post-colonial continuum in terms of notions of progress and modernity. By putting two bodies of literature from contemporary Black/African studies and STS in conversation, this paper aims at opening up new ways for STS to interrogate knowledge production practices of AI from a Black/African studies perspective.

Complicating Narratives of Afro-Asian Solidarity: A "Distant Reading" of the 1955 Bandung Conference Proceedings *Nikhil Dharmaraj, Harvard College*

In this project, I utilize "distant reading" techniques, as described by scholar Franco Morretti, to complicate the narrative of Afro-Asian solidarity at the 1955 Bandung Conference. Despite the undeniable significance of Bandung as the first large-scale gathering of Afro-Asian states, often missing in historical interpretations of this conference is the calculus of anti-Blackness, anti-Indigeneity, patriarchy, neocolonialism, and bourgeois nationalisms — all of which destabilize idyllic understandings of post-colonial solidarity at the conference. Utilizing methods of natural language processing (NLP), I conduct a digital humanities analysis of archival documents relating to the Bandung conference to quantify the extent to which Afro-Asian solidarity was truly operational at the 1955 Bandung Conference. In substance, my work designs a novel, generalizable computational model of solidarity, amalgamating known NLP methods — such as sentiment analysis, word embeddings, implicit bias testing, and the Python question-intimacy package — to output two-dimensional quantifications of solidarity. In digitally analyzing the proceedings of the Bandung conference in 1955, this project also serves to illuminate how artificial intelligence (AI) can be repurposed as a tool of radical, decolonial storytelling. I utilize computational techniques to not only contextualize the Bandung narrative, but also, to illuminate more authentic ways of constructing networks of solidarity in the current moment. My project, then, ontologically highlights the role that digital humanities/"distant reading" can play within Science and Technology Studies — that is, understanding computation as a potential means to learn from decolonial histories and literatures.

Session Organizer:

Noopur Raval

Chair:

Ranjit Pal Singh, Data & Society Research Institute

Discussant:

Sareeta Amrute, University of Washington

046. Markets as data - I - Algorithms, data streams and trade

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

STS scholars have long been interested in the diverse devices that equip markets, from market infrastructures to mundane marketing tools such as shopping carts, knowledge devices, and measuring instruments. As markets are digitized, consumer records, scoring and targeting instruments, trading

machines, and so on are key to how markets operate. Data act as a versatile, yet vital, apparatus for markets, playing crucial roles in the form of devices, valuation tools, infrastructures, and assets. This panel will explore these various facets of data, and how they help to bring markets into being. We welcome empirical and theoretical investigations of markets as data. First, with big data technologies, marketing knowledge is increasingly produced from the analysis of large databases that combine heterogeneous arrays of information on consumers, products, firms, and market operations. These data are then stabilized through metrics, dashboards and standards. How do these new “data objects” and knowledge devices reconfigure practices? Second, data streams are fueling automation or decision-making systems: matching algorithms, trade desks, recommendation engines, smart contracts, market screening mechanisms, dashboards. How does automation reconfigure firms’ practices in markets? Third, data are increasingly marketized themselves, harvested from public-facing services such as social media. How do markets for data impact “conventional” markets? Finally, data practices are increasingly subject to specific governance that is often the object of fierce contestation: from regulation such as GDPR in Europe, industry-level self-regulation and labelling processes, to local framing within firms. How does the governance of data, and its contestation shape markets and marketization practices?

Participants:

Intimate Auctions: "Header Bidding" and the Material Political Economy of Digital Advertising *Donald MacKenzie, University Of Edinburgh*

Billions of times daily, a user’s actions in an app, social media platform or search engine trigger a near-instantaneous auction of the opportunity to show that user an advertisement. These auctions are intimate in two senses. First, bids are informed by gigantic datastreams carrying information about each action, its context, and – if a “cookie” (Mellet and Beauvisage 2019) or other identifier is available – the individual user. Second, some auctions are conducted not by distant computer servers, but by the user’s own phone, tablet or laptop (devices that their owners often regard as deeply personal), normally without the user’s awareness. This paper will place “client-side header bidding” – advertising auctions conducted by users’ devices – within the overall history of advertising auctions and of conflict over material arrangements and market dominance in digital advertising. For example, header bidding largely circumvents Google’s systems, and was presented to publishers as a way of increasing their share of advertising revenues. Google’s reaction to its emergence is prominent in anti-trust critiques of Google (especially Srinivasan 2020) and the lawsuit launched in December by Republican attorneys general. The paper draws on 18 interviews conducted by the author – hopefully substantially more by the time 4S meets – and participation in seven advertising-sector industry meetings. The paper’s theoretical contribution will be to return to the debate over the performativity of economics (auction theory is prominent in modern economics), arguing for the need to deepen this literature’s emphasis on materiality and political contestation and to develop an STS-inflected conceptualisation of “market power.”

Tailoring Digital Markets: Tokens Issuances As Valuation Processes In Algorithmic Platformization *Clement Gasull, ECOLE DES MINES DE PARIS*

Give a look at a dashboard listing ‘cryptocurrencies’ by their market capitalizations and you’ll see billions of dollars associated to trigrams. Some of them are ‘utility tokens’. Buy one and you may get ownership over any kind of physical or digital object, be it physical gold or distributed computation. Switch marketplace and you may invest in financial instruments called ‘security tokens’ or may fall for a unique digital piece of art represented by a ‘collectible’. Any of them is a digital, tradable and marketable asset. All are implemented in the form of smart contracts, algorithms written in a single programming language and interact through a shared distributed ledger called

Ethereum. Along with token exchange platforms, Telegram groups, Slack channels, Meetups among other in-person events, Ethereum is part of a sociotechnical assemblage that makes as many markets as tokens come into being. Drawing on STS and social studies of finance, this paper analyses this seemingly market-speaking machinery as a ductile marketization platform by examining chains of operations leading to tokens issuances. Tokens and their markets are configured by social practices and valuation processes (Muniesa 2011) involving very specific actors, business models, regulations and standards depending on their class (utility, security, collectible). In discussion with works analysing financial activity in contemporary technoscientific capitalism in terms of processes of financialization, capitalization and assetization (Birch 2017), the paper suggests to consider innovative forms of algorithms such as smart contracts as objects of valuation to analyse such processes in the digital economy.

The Bloomberg Terminal *Ignacio Choi*

The Bloomberg Terminal, some preliminary observations and outlook into a deeper investigation Contrary to expectations of ubiquitous data, in real life, collecting and consolidating data takes work and produces striated and heterogeneous archives. Such efforts are historically organized in specific complexes, “data works.” In the contemporary world of finance, the most important such “work” is the Bloomberg Terminal. For any serious professional participant in the financial markets, The Terminal is the way the global economy becomes visible; and in the routine practice of the financial industries, the global economy is “what can be seen on the Bloomberg Terminal” (although market professionals also try to gain an edge by accessing data that are not represented on The Terminal.) Any asset, instrument, or commodity that is traded internationally is likely to be represented on the Terminal, and such inclusion is at the same time a key condition for an asset to be able to be valued and traded in international markets. As an institution that shapes the perception and the workings of global markets, the Terminal deserves its own investigation. I describe some key features of the Terminal, raise what I think are some key questions, and attempt to present a roadmap for future research. One aspect that deserves mention is the way in which at present human traders perform the work of integrating heterogeneous data streams presented by The Terminal, such as past pricing data and mathematically derived “metrics,” and macroeconomic news data, and prospects for change in the future.

Should algorithms manage markets? Market and algorithmic opacity in mediated markets *Andrew Chong, UC Berkeley School of Information*

This article discusses market opacity, and how it relates to growing concerns over algorithmic transparency and explainability. I explore the different ways mediation - where markets are constructed and managed by code - complicates views of market fairness. I apply discourse analysis to how different stakeholders justify or object to the use of algorithms in markets, and how competing principles of fairness may be used to justify different practices to consumers, workers, regulators and other stakeholders. I group these concerns under four main classifications - deontological and utilitarian, procedural and distributive. I argue that where optimization increasingly occurs via highly managed, highly engineered complex systems, where utilitarian maximization is not easily verifiable in practice or by economic theory, we see a turn to deontology to justify preferences around marketplace principles - eschewing utilitarian considerations. I in turn argue that the capability of markets to function as a mechanism for distributive and procedural fairness is constrained and under threat in mediated markets. I introduce the concept of norms engineering, where firms may superficially modify marketplace principles to evade normative concerns by stakeholders, or seek to influence those norms themselves. I center the importance of socio-technical mechanisms by which mediated markets may be governed to serve collective social

goals, and to better capture the fairness concerns of different stakeholders. I situate the larger question of how mediated markets - markets constructed and managed with code - may serve as a tool for society, mapping to and extending beyond current debates over platform governance.

Session Organizers:

Thomas Beauvisage, Orange Labs
Donald MacKenzie, University Of Edinburgh
Kevin Mellet, Sciences Po - CSO
Zsuzsanna Vargha, ESCP Business School

Chair:

Kevin Mellet, Sciences Po - CSO

047. Pandemic Breathing – Air as Matter of Dis/Connection I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

In times of the covid-19-pandemic air becomes an element known for its aerosols being capable of passing a virus mouth-to-mouth. It is obvious that air is an element of connection, an interface where humans and more-than-humans, bodies and the world interfere (cf. Adey 2014, Allen 2020, Baake 2018, Górka 2016). Air is pure complexity: it is full of relations, it is a microcosm composed of heterogeneous elements. But air is also a boundless matter difficult to discipline. During the pandemic human breathing has become a matter of disconnecting physical bodies that should keep a distance measured in meters or whose exhalations should only meet filtered by a mask. But what happens in filtering practices and can they be studied as a nature-culture separation processes? Moreover, '[a]ll air is not equal' (Godfrey & Torres, 2016: 9), since the air in urban areas is polluted, not everyone can afford ventilation systems or simply because lung volumes vary. The corona crisis has exposed the socio-spatial, political and economic aspects of breathing. It changes our thoughtless relationship with the air and is a burning lens that makes both microscopic connections and dis-connections visible. With our talk we would like to discuss this double character of air using various examples.

Participants:

Breathing Troubles in Covid-19: Im/Mobile Bodies, Nomadic Imagination, and Planetary Health *Nasima Selim, Freie Universität Berlin*

Pandemics are one among many planetary specters haunting us. Its ethnographic articulation necessitates the thick description of more-than-human elements. The pandemic has made it difficult to breathe, let alone write about interrupted fieldwork and livelihood. Breathing is not only an autonomic bodily function but a biosocial practice, historically situated, geographically constituted, and materially embedded within human and nonhuman bodies. To breathe in a Covid-19 afflicted planet is to inspire and expire droplets with hypermobile viral bodies, the invisible breath of plants, the increasingly toxic urban air, and the atmosphere of structural racism (with other forms of intersectional inequalities). The bodily and metaphorical extensions of breathing troubles in a pandemic are co-constitutive of our postcolonial predicament in the Racial Capitalocene where the global South suffers from historical injustice (Vergès 2017). Research and writing during Covid-19 require the mobilization of nomadic imagination and a critical lens toward planetary health. I draw an ethnographic example from my exploratory fieldwork in India that Covid-19 interrupted, catapulting career aspirations in jeopardy. I cannot write ethnographically about this pandemic without the intensities of breathing and the ingredients of affective, sensuous scholarship (Selim 2021, Stodulka, Selim, and Mattes 2018; Stoller 1997). The contexts where we study the politics and socio-materiality of breathing invite the questions of poetics and creative imagination. In addition to material practices enacted by pandemic breathing, this paper will offer preliminary insights into vernacular and scientific imagination practices of more-than-human breathing in the pandemic era.

Labour Like Lichen: Air Healthcare, Multispecies Performance,

and the Queering of Ecosystem Services *Alexandra R. Toland, Bauhaus Universität Weimar; Beate Körner, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar; Harriet Von Froreich, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar*

Any lichen will tell you: air has agency. It is a complex body made up of different gasses and aerosols, pressures and particles, movements and moods. It roams freely and interacts with other bodies such as soil, water, humans and other life forms. But keeping air healthy takes work. This labour includes policies to reduce emissions, activism to hold policy-makers accountable, biofiltration functions performed by trees and bushes, bioindication "signposting" services carried out by lichen, mosses and birds, and the cooling work of global water systems. Ecosystem Services (ESS), or the "services" provided by nature for the well-being of humans, are one way of imagining the non-human labour involved in keeping air healthy. However, the human-centric framing of the ESS paradigm as well as the patriarchal and colonial roots of "service" as an organising concept potentially hinder alternative modes of valuing nature, for example in commoning, gift economies, rights to nature, etc. This paper examines how artists performatively respond to air pollution, showing how "service" can be provoked, mediated, affected, disassembled, and reinterpreted to challenge the status quo. We propose a theory of "Queering Ecosystem Services" that 1) surveys the types of activities that get defined or dismissed as ecosystem services, especially as they relate to air 2) draws on examples of performance art to explore the agencies of those doing the defining, soliciting and providing of services, and finally 3) experimentally integrates methods of performance art to propose alternative approaches to air-health "services" inspired by the sensitive, symbiotic labour of lichen.

Attuning to Atmospheres *Desiree Förster, University of Chicago*

In this paper I will reflect on the meaning of atmospheres while the human world has been overwhelmed by a respiratory disease. In an auto-ethnographic gesture I reflect different ways of sensing and becoming sensitive to the atmospheric changes in my home during self-isolation. This self-questioning is directly related to the conceptualization of air in view of its potential risk of carrying infectious virus particles. The air we breathe is currently stylized as a cloud on the micro-level of aerosols, which gives reason to think anew about the status of the atmospheric with regard to our being in the world. Through combining philosophical reflection with aesthetic practice I explore how an attunement towards the ways air flows through our habitats can open a new perspective on processes of subjectivation in a time of ongoing crisis. I argue that becoming sensitive towards airflow not only heightens our sensitivity for the affectivity of atmospheric processes but also for the different registers of our experience able to capture these effects.

(In)visible Substances. Air And Its Materiality In Natural Science Lessons *Anna Dorn, Johannes Gutenberg-University Mainz*

As any other being, humans are surrounded by substances – solids, powders, liquids and gas. They can be clearly visible as in the case of water, cooking oil, and drugs, for example, or be hidden from our perception such as undesirable toxins in children's toys. The aim of my paper is to discuss a potential sociological perspective on whether and how invisible substances such as air, can be theoretically and empirically conceptualised. Therefore, this paper examines the involvement of substances in laboratory practice with respect to its materiality, using natural science lessons as an empirical case. Chemical substances are ubiquitous in natural science lessons. As material entities, air and other gases are embedded in manifold practices between bodies, objects, fluids and solids. My paper explores two different aspects of these intangible and gaseous substances and their involvement in experimental practices: Firstly, the manipulation

of their material features and qualities. Students use their breathe in order to differentiate between acids and bases. Secondly, their visualisation and representation. Invisible substances need particular tracers to become visible, thus empirically observable with respect to certain alterations. Breathing in the water can cause a chemical reaction only ascertainable by indicators. In consequence, puffed breath – air – has an impact in experimental arrangements and therefore emerges specific connections between bodies, expertise, technical objects and further substances. The presented empirical data derive from participant observations of school lessons and guided experimentations in a university student lab.

Doing Critical Air Quality Science In Times Of COVID
Douglas David Booker, Lancaster University; gordon Walker; Paul Young, Lancaster University

Through the delivery of an indoor air quality (IAQ) monitoring project in 20 schools around the UK (pre and post COVID-19 emergence), aimed at understanding the ‘real-world’ effectiveness of air filtering technologies, this paper will demonstrate how the emergence of airborne SARS-CoV-2 fundamentally altered the socio-material assemblage of school IAQ, highlighting its reconfigured relations with human and material practices, social and natural rhythms, and technologies. With a proliferation of IAQ monitoring projects aimed at designating air as ‘COVID safe’, this paper argues for a ‘critical air quality science’ that acknowledges the material significance of IAQ (e.g. transmission of COVID-19) by doing physical air quality science, but also embraces the hybridity (material and cultural / social) and multiplicity of IAQ (Bickerstaff, 2004; Cupples, 2009; Garnett, 2017). To do a critical air quality science, I ‘follow myself’ through the process of doing physical air quality science and employ a ‘near ANT’ (Farias, Blok, & Roberts, 2020) approach to use ANT concepts as a source of questions, problems and inspiration to think through the social and natural of IAQ in a hybrid way (Cupples, 2009). This rich, reflexive, and hybrid view of IAQ science in action reveals the connections that were (re)made in the process of measuring and making IAQ breathable in times of COVID. It is envisaged that this critical air quality science approach can ensure that appropriate socio-material interventions are made whilst ensuring that the reconfiguring of school IAQ does not exacerbate existing air inequalities.

Session Organizers:

Vanessa Weber, Hafencity University
Lisa Wiedemann, Helmut Schmidt University Hamburg

Chairs:

Vanessa Weber, Hafencity University
Lisa Wiedemann, Helmut Schmidt University Hamburg

048. Practices And Methods Towards Good Relations With Robots And AI II

9:40 to 11:10 am
4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Participants:

Practicing Feminist Robotics in “Indispensable” *Katherine Behar, Baruch College, City University of New York*
Taking “Indispensable”—an interactive art installation featuring a re-engineered automatic hand sanitizer dispenser—as a case study, I discuss how interactive art and feminist robotics converge to promote “good relations with robots and AI.” “Indispensable” promotes feminist solidarities with other-than-human robotic devices, while encouraging viewers to value affective care work. Additionally, its development process with engineering and art students at University of Michigan, intentionally supplants STEM’s oppressive norms with feminist values of inclusive solidarity. Literally “giving voice” to an automatic hand sanitizer dispenser, “Indispensable” imagines

what the device might think silently to itself when human supplicants approach it with outstretched empty hands. This hand gesture triggers voice recordings considering the situation from the dispenser’s point of view. Varying in tone, the dispenser’s statements convey its grumpy mood, loving mood, or somewhere between. After hearing what the dispenser has to say, viewers rate their experience at a customer feedback kiosk. Positive or negative ratings “move the needle” of the dispenser’s personality so that subsequent statements become increasingly affectionate and caring, or surly and disgruntled. “Indispensable” explores our ambiguous relationship with dispensers. When we take their work for granted, dispensers become unsung providers of care work, suggesting parallels between “indispensable dispensers” and human “essential workers.” Further, when we approach dispensers with begging, cupped-hand gestures to save us from contagion, we empower them as god-like oracles, exposing the uncertainty and fragility of human survival. Ultimately, we remain “indispensable” to one another—after all, “automatic” devices can’t perform without human hands to trigger them.

Shaping Relationships By Imagining Users: What A Commercial Can Tell Us About Practices Between Voice Assistants And Users. *Bettina Pospisil, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies*

Nowadays, our everyday life is permeated by intelligent technologies, participating in the most private parts of people’s lives. Especially voice assistants (e.g. Alexa) - providing us with the possibility of linguistic interactions - are becoming important actors of user’s everyday lives with deep impact on practices and relationships. By now, we know little about how users perceive and give meaning to their relationships with voice assistants and how those are enacted through practices. Drawing on the approach of inscription (Akrich 1992; Latour 1988), this paper follows the assumption, that user’s relations with voice assistants are next to others shaped by user-roles inscribed in voice assistants. To shed light on these inscribed user-roles, I enacted a qualitative video analysis of a commercial of the exemplary voice assistant Amazon Alexa. Drawing on actor-network-theory (ANT), this research work takes a symmetrical approach focusing on non-human actors as voice assistants as well as human actors as users. To apply this view onto the method of the video analysis, I use the HANOS partitur (Reichert & Englert 2011; Moritz 2011) focusing on the practices of non-humans (e.g. camera) as well as humans (e.g. performer) and adjusted it to my research interest. This paper will investigate, from an empirical perspective, how developers imagine users of voice assistants as well as their practices and relations with the devices. Thus, the findings of the paper will contribute to ongoing discussions in the field of STS on how inscribed user-roles and imaginations shape users practices and relations.

Wagging tails & fur: On the changing function of animal references in consumer robots advertisements *Philipp Graf, Technische Universität Chemnitz; Britta Schulte, Bauhaus Universität Weimar*

Specific terms in the field of HRI like “zoomorphic design”, “perceived animacy” (Carpinella, Wyman, Perez, & Stroessner, 2017) or the categorization as “Bio-Inspired” (IEEE, 2021; Romano, Donati, Benelli, & Stefanini, 2019) clearly point to the fact, that robotics reflexively incorporates animal references. Through a systematic analysis of commercial videos of consumer robots of the last 20 years we review the specific forms, contextualization, and interrelations of animal references in consumer robots advertisement (Ingram & Annable, 2004) and how their motivation changed and diversified over time. We focus on the explicitly ascribed animal characteristics and user relations and through these explore which understanding of nature/culture they implicitly assume and set. We start with the premise that at the advent of consumer robotics we can observe a strong focus on a re-engineering of the whole animal as such,

including a replication of distinct complex characteristics of lifelike animals. This form of reference decreased in the later years (Kwak, San, Jung, & Choi, 2017). Instead, we expect to find an increased inscription of certain characteristics associated with specific animals that are reflexively linked to the social functionalities they shall effectively fulfill for the user. We argue that this can be described as an increase of a fragmental use of animal characteristics and ask the question, how this points to qualitatively new construction of ontological categories like “animal”, “robot” and “being” (Alač, Movellan, & Tanaka, 2011) and how this could affect the relationship between humans with both artificial and non-artificial entities.

Motivational Algorithms: Appraising Taxonomies of Trust in a Counselling Chatbot *Mathew Iantorno, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto; Olivia Doggett, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto; Camille Intson, University of Toronto; Matt Ratto, University of Toronto*

As the algorithms and data sets driving conversational user interfaces (CUIs) have advanced, there has been a growing interest in utilizing these technologies beyond the transactional exchanges seen in virtual assistants. Researchers for the Centre for Addiction and Mental Health (CAMH) in Toronto, Canada – in collaboration with our team and computer science students and faculty at the University of Toronto – are currently developing a chatbot aimed to assist users with smoking cessation. This chatbot leverages the robust Generative Pre-trained Transformer 3 (GPT-3) autoregressive language model alongside other natural language processing (NLP) technologies, such as GPT-2 and BERT. By adopting the client-centred counselling approach of motivational interviewing (MI), the artificial intelligence (AI) driven chatbot is intended to provide an accessible alternative to an appointment with a human therapist. This paper examines how the transposition of a chatbot into this clinical role creates unique challenges in appraising the development of trust within the relationship. Taxonomies of trust commonly adapted for science and technology studies research are often designed exclusively for human-human or human-machine interaction, leaving little affordance for technologies intended to directly emulate human conversation and empathetic domains of experience. By applying one human- and one machine-oriented taxonomy of trust to the pilot study of the smoking cessation chatbot, this paper proposes new concerns for gauging trust when embodied human ability is translated into a disembodied digital space. Four such concerns for behavioural intervention chatbots are examined: (1) predictability, (2) expert knowledge, (3) clinical context, and (4) human experience.

Session Organizers:

Andreas Bischof, University of Technology Chemnitz
Arne Maibaum, TU Berlin

049. Metaexpertise? STS, Metascience, and Data Science - II: The Possibilities and Dangers of Meta-expertise

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

The past decade has seen efforts to develop new forms of “domain-general” expertise such as metascience and data science. These have different motivations and intervene in specific fields in different ways—as interlocutors, partners, and, even, diagnosticians. Often, different forms of expertise establish distinct epistemic cultures in order to protect their autonomy and avoid the open conflicts that reveal rival epistemological commitments. However, interactions between domain-general and domain-specific forms of expertise have produced new conflicts. This raises challenging questions. Does the incursion of domain-general expertise represent a threat to the autonomy of disciplinary scientists? What would ‘good relations’ across this divide look like? How are domain-specific skills like embodied knowledge and practical judgment absorbed into domain-general systems meant to enumerate, evaluate, or automate scientific practice? The three sessions in this panel explore how these new

“sciences of science” are transforming knowledge making.

Participants:

Translating Across Domains in Biomedical Research:

Interoperability, Semantic Violence, and Closure Work in Systems Design *Andrew Staver Hoffman, iHub, Radboud University Nijmegen*

In the vernacular of contemporary data science, ‘interoperability’ is posited as a guiding principle for the conduct of data-intensive work, and its adjectival rendering – ‘interoperable’ – the quality ascribed to entities that can be more or less seamlessly fused together despite initially appearing in divergent formats and/or emanating from different domains. Meanwhile, in biomedical research parlance, ‘translation’ has traditionally been used to describe the set of processes through which insights and discoveries made in basic or fundamental research are transformed – or ‘translated,’ as it were – into clinically actionable interventions, such as the development or repurposing of pharmaceuticals, diagnostics, and behavioral interventions. A closer look at the policies and practices driving contemporary translational science reveals that there is a process of synonymization underway whereby ‘translation’ and ‘interoperation’ are becoming increasingly indistinguishable terms. This paper empirically unpacks this shift, drawing from ongoing ethnographic fieldwork with a federally-funded consortium whose members are collectively building a next-generation question answering tool – part smart assistant, part expert system – whose ultimate goal is to streamline the research process such that therapies can be found more quickly and patients can be treated more effectively. Given that this tool relies upon semantic technologies to mutually translate the diversity of ‘languages’ spoken by different biomedical communities, our analysis attends to the work practices that facilitate semantic interoperability in a complex sociotechnical system, outlining a set of frictions and closure mechanisms wherein the ‘stickiness of difference’ (Poirier 2015) across domains is rendered a tractable problem.

The Future of Neuroimaging and AI-assisted Neuroimaging for Dementia Diagnosis: results from a Thematic Analysis and a Neuroanthropology approach *N. Elida Defurth, York University, Canada*

Intense research efforts over exceptionally large neuroimaging datasets are currently targeting the development of novel algorithms for pattern recognition in the diagnosis of Alzheimer’s disease and other dementias. Brain connectivity is a prominent theme in research studies highlighting recent advances in AI-assisted neuroimaging employing non-invasive MRI. Researchers target functional and structural neural activity to explain neurological disorders from a connectivity standpoint. Studies also use brain atlases containing multi-modal data with the goal of detecting signs of neurological disease. Brain mapping atlases support specific brain areas, populations, and meta-data configurations which contribute to enabling data-sharing and the use of powerful computational tools for data modelling and analysis. As these efforts continue to evolve towards more ambitious goals such as the inclusion of genetic mapping in combination with brain mapping, the expectations indicate that specialized brain data repositories coupled with Machine Learning algorithms for classification and analysis will revolutionize not only our understanding of the brain but also the diagnosis and treatment of neurodegenerative diseases. Studies focusing on performance analyses between AI and human clinical experts are shedding light over the extent of application of AI to disease diagnoses (Shen et al. 2019). ML diagnostic algorithms are thought to produce performances comparable and even superior to medical experts, especially in image recognition. My research examines the challenges of categorising expert knowledge from STS and neuroanthropology standpoints while offering a sociotechnical perspective on assessment and adoption

of AI-driven methods in dementia diagnosis.

The Resolution of Epistemic Crises in Biomedicine: The Stage of Transparency *Alexander Constantin Schniedermann, Deutsches Zentrum für Hochschul- und Wissenschaftsforschung, Hannover; Bluemel Clemens, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies*

Representing “the totality of the evidence” (Ioannidis 2005, 125), meta-analyzing and systematic reviewing was once coined as ‘the platinum standard of evidence’ that thrones all evidence hierarchies. Usually, they are understood as tools of ordering research and parts of a complex machinery that transforms knowledge into evidence. They do so by valuing specific types of research such as clinical trials which they aim to observe and evaluate at the same time. But systematic reviewing also involves procedures of quantification, such as technologies of screening, identifying and assessing studies in a process that turns quantities into qualities: objectivity is constructed by the maximization of included studies or measurements. In our study, we explored the emergence and transformation of these tools of ordering and their ways of operating. One of the sources by which systematic reviews maintain their legitimacy are guidelines for reporting and conduct. Especially the development and promotion of reporting guidelines is related to various debates about transparency and quality in biomedical research – debates that also transformed the goals and means of systematic reviews. Observing this movement and its motives, we performed document analyses of one of the most prominent reporting standards and its reflexive discussion, the PRISMA guideline. To further understand how transparency is perceived to preserve or replace traditional epistemic virtues, we also performed expert interviews with developers of the guideline. Ioannidis, J. P. A. (2005). Why Most Published Research Findings Are False.

Session Organizer:

Martin Bush, University of Melbourne

Chair:

David Peterson, UCLA

050. Computational Media Technologies: Computing and Critique Beyond Disciplinary Configurations - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Despite the ongoing interest in the history, epistemology, sociology, and cultures of computing and its defining practices (see Benjamin 2019, Mackenzie 2001, Roberge & Castelle 2020), the study of computational media remains largely dispersed across a wide range of discipline specific venues. Inspired by the more systemic examinations of computing advanced by fields like critical AI studies, indigenous STS, and media anthropology, however, this open panel brings together scholars who share a similar interest in understanding the transdisciplinary complexities, alternative histories, and political a priors behind computational media. With that intention in mind, we propose to consider computation as a paradigmatic ‘media technology’ whose entanglement with questions of both mediation and technoscience promises to renew the study of technical cultures at large. Computational media, we contend, provides a rich, boundary (defying) object around which the disciplinary perspective of media studies, history of technology, and science studies can be made to converge. Not only does computational media relate contemporary technoscience to the cybernetic and cyborgial origins of computing (see Haraway 1985, Hayles 1999, Medina 2011), it also forces us to consider mediation as a structuring principle of technoscientific cultures, practices, and epistemologies (see Kittler 1986, Chun 2011). To explore these questions, this open panel will stage a number of interdisciplinary conversations which will not only revisit dominant discourses surrounding the study of computational media, but also challenge the disciplinary frameworks in which they have been historically concentrated.

Participants:

Computers and You: Constructing Women as Habitual Users in the 1980s *Myrna A Moretti, Northwestern University*

Media studies scholars often historicize cultural attitudes about early personal computing and video gaming through sensational and anxious texts like TRON, WarGames, and Neuromancer. This approach is limited, both because it centers white men and it overlooks the fact that during the 1980s and early 1990s personal computers and other electronics were purchased at an exponential rate in the United States—despite potential anxiety. My paper works to decenter this canon through a feminist cultural history approach informed by current new media theory. Scholars including Wendy Hui Kyong Chun, James J. Hodge, Lisa Nakamura, and Scott Richmond broadly consider how the increasing ubiquity of computing and digital technology have made media ordinary.(1) Through primary source discourse analysis, my paper shows that habit and habituation were a key way that films, television shows, magazines, and advertisements for women positioned technology as ordinary. As a case study I examine the Black womens’ magazine *Essence* during the 1980s. *Essence* published articles and columns including “Tech Knowledge” and “Computers and You” that suggested how readers might easily incorporate computers into their professional and personal lives. In the October 1983 article, “Ready or Not, Here Comes the Computer Future,” Rosemary L. Bray writes that “a computer is only a combination of tools we’ve used all our lives without a second thought.” Comments like this position the computer as open for habituation and within the reader’s existing skill set. My analysis extends current new media theory into the preceding technological era and, as Jennifer S. Light argues, “write[s] women back into the history they were always a part of.”(2) 1. For Lauren Berlant ‘ordinary’ suggests the context of neoliberalism and late capitalism compared to the ‘everyday’ which is a response to industrialization and modernity. See Cruel Optimism, (Durham: Duke University Press, 2011), 6-10. 2. Jennifer S. Light, “When Women Were Computers,” *Technology and Culture* 40, no. 3 (July 1999): 483.

Fans, Fans Everywhere: Towards a thermal media theory of computation *Ranjodh Singh Dhaliwal, University of Notre Dame*

This talk starts with the curious yet banal observation that over the last few decades, more and more of computational space in the machine has been occupied by thermal mechanisms. Heat sinks, fans, thermal pastes all spread over our motherboards in ever-expanding formations, at the same time as (and because of) the microprocessors and memory devices shrink. What makes heat management such an important part of the computer, I argue, is not only that it is a huge problem for computer scientists, something to be aspirationally designed away, but also that it marks an integral part of what computation ‘is.’ Culling through a history of the computational heatsink, and its interrelations with histories of microprocessors and computer graphics (through data centers and render farms), I offer a framework under which computation can be understood ‘as’ a thermal, a thermodynamic, process. In doing so, I contribute to an increasingly important part of media technology studies that understands technology through its material, infrastructural effects, building on work around computing and heat by the likes of Finn Brunton, Jim Malazita, Nicole Starosielski, Jussi Parikka, Nathan Ensmenger, and Mél Hogan. Computational media technologies, here, show up to not be in the process of contributing to global warming by a side-effectual causality but because computational techno-logics encode and invite an engagement with heat. In other words, computation is cool (cf. Alan Liu) because computers are hot.

Green Grass Computation *Abelardo Gil-Fournier, FAMU, Prague; Jussi Parikka, University of Southampton and FAMU, Prague*

From references in science fiction (Asimov, LeGuin, Robbins) to

popular images such as the Windows bliss wallpaper, the image of grass has its own life in representations and fictions of computational media and artificial intelligence. Furthermore, current literature in the Plant Sciences (Trewavas, Mancuso) and Plant Studies (Marder) have discussed extensively topics such as vegetal signalling, intelligence and plant thinking. In this paper we seek to approach grass as computational media through an elaboration of the concept of the managerial surface, proposed by John May as a response to current practices in environmental sciences and landscape design, where imaging and modelling collide in a “statistical-electrical control space” (2020). While the observation of certain vegetal patterns in remote sensing is correlated to specific features of the terrain (Pietrusko), the systematic registration of greenness as Green Chromatic Coordinates (GCC), Leaf Area Index (LAI) and Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) present vegetal surfaces as a form of computational mediation at the landscape scale. We argue that grass presents a case where this connection between imaging and modelling can be understood in relation to discussions that relate early photography and computation (Batchen 2002, 2006) and recent accounts in history of science about statistics and experimental practices (Coen 2007, 2018). Such historical references build a case that helps to understand both the speculative proposal in this paper about green grass computation and the empirical practices where colour coded surfaces are a particular kind of a computational image at a landscape scale.

Pokémon, no? Or the Digital Cultures of Valuing Biodiversity
Thomas Patrick Pringle, Tulane University

How does an augmented reality smartphone game premised on collecting and exchanging virtual monsters shed light on the ongoing “biological annihilation” of the sixth mass extinction event? This presentation approaches Pokémon Go through two critical genealogies: capitalist efforts to assign monetary value to species biodiversity as a part of ecosystem service economies and American techno-utopian environmentalists who understand biodiversity as something prone to archival storage, equating genetic code with the reanimating properties of digital information. The game received a warm scholarly reception in conservation biology, where several articles celebrated the use of smart-phones as a potential model to gamify and peer-produce citizen science. By constellating and historicizing the game’s scientific reception, this paper expounds the conditions of knowledge necessary for Pokémon Go to be thought of as a model for participatory conservation engagement. In particular, I show how biologist E. O. Wilson’s capitalist rendering of biodiversity as valuable information affected Kevin Kelly and Stewart Brand’s All-Species Inventory (2000), an unsuccessful attempt to use networked personal computing to create a complete taxonomic inventory of the world’s wildlife for conservation. I hold this history in parallel with American efforts to finance ecosystem biodiversity as a part of neoliberal environmental economics, which locate monetary value in species existence for the corporate evaluation of ecological risk. In creating, valuing, and mapping a virtual ecosystem of monsters for sale and storage, Pokémon Go ambivalently signals the relationship between informational capitalism, the cultural valuation of animal life, and the digital lamination of a catastrophic material reality.

Playing with Fire: The Production and Management of Heat through the Unreal Engine
James Malazita, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

This talk presents a “Critical Platform Studies” analysis of the Unreal Engine, a complex arrangement software, hardware, institutions, and practices that guides the digital game development process. I argue that one of Unreal’s primary infrastructural responsibilities in game development practice is the epistemic production and management of heat. Following insights from “STS Underground” literatures, Feminist New

Materialisms, and Nicole Starosielski’s concept of thermocultures, I demonstrate that Unreal works by first producing “heat itself” as a resource, and further translating that heat across an array of other resource productions. Heat becomes made knowable through a multitude of affective and phenomenological indices: such as the affective measurement of heat via “Frames per Second” metrics, internal tracking of computational “Operations per Tick,” thermo-readings of GPU video cards and their heat syncs, and fan and case management. Game developers use Unreal to play with heat. As games near completion, developer work largely shifts from asset production to computational efficiency management. This means using Unreal’s internal tools, third party software, and technical tricks of the trade to minimize software computations and distribute heat across various components of a computer’s hardware so that the game runs as smoothly for the player as possible. Unreal thus operates as a nexus point in a broader flow of heat across bodies, electronics, indices, and player experiences.

Session Organizers:

Théo Lepage-Richer, Brown University
Ranjodh Singh Dhaliwal, University of Notre Dame

Chair:

Ranjodh Singh Dhaliwal, University of Notre Dame

051. Preparing for Human Genome Editing Technologies

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

The rapid development of human genome editing (HGE) technologies has raised significant questions about these tools’ potential and proper applications and societal impacts, as well as broader practical and philosophical questions of authority, governance, control and future-making around technological innovation in society. High-profile expert statements and consensus reports have stressed the importance of forward-looking policy development and deliberative public engagement to guide the future of HGE. Forward-looking, democratically oriented governance is encouraged to ensure that any applications of genome editing to humans serve rather than undercut public values. We present early results emerging from an NIH-funded grant that applies strategies of anticipatory governance for inclusive, values-based expert and public engagement and future-oriented reflection around the development and governance of HGE. Research began with qualitative interviews probing how experts and stakeholders think about pressing ethical, social and political dilemmas and their views on the dominant drivers of change. Next, experts and stakeholders were convened to generate a small set of plausible scenarios supporting critical reflection about access and equity, biosecurity, eugenics, trust and the political economy of innovation. By embedding HGE technologies in alternative socio-political contexts, the scenarios work to transform deep and multi-dimensional uncertainties attending HGE into tractable stories to facilitate critical appraisal. Last, in preparation for upcoming deliberative forums designed to enable publics to voice their perspectives, an open framing deliberative mapping was conducted. Together these efforts represent a set of practices that are designed to support the inclusion of diverse perspectives in the construction of better policy.

Participants:

Toward Anticipatory Governance of Human Genome Editing
John P. Nelson, School for Future of Innovation in Society, Arizona State University; Cynthia Selin, Arizona State University; Christopher Thomas Scott, Baylor College of Medicine

The rapid development of human genome editing (HGE) techniques evokes an urgent need for forward-looking deliberation regarding the aims, processes, and governance of research. The framework of anticipatory governance may serve this need. This article reviews scholarly discourse about HGE through an anticipatory governance lens, aiming to identify gaps in discussion and practice and suggest how AG efforts may fill them. Discourse on HGE has insufficiently reckoned with the

institutional and systemic contexts, inputs, and implications of HGE work, to the detriment of its ability to prepare for a variety of possible futures and pursue socially desirable ones. More broadly framed and inclusive efforts in foresight and public engagement, focused not only upon the in-principle permissibility of HGE activities but upon the contexts of such work, may permit improved identification of public values relevant to HGE and of actions by which researchers, funders, policymakers, and publics may promote them.

Experts' Insights and Foresights on Human Genome Editing
Dorit Barlevy, Baylor College of Medicine; Stephanie Morain, Baylor College of Medicine; Haley Manley, Baylor College of Medicine; John P. Nelson, School for Future of Innovation in Society, Arizona State University; Cynthia Selin, Arizona State University; Christopher Thomas Scott, Baylor College of Medicine

The rapid pace of research and development of human genome editing (HGE) raises significant ethical, legal, and social challenges. As part of a study that aims to propose governance policies that anticipate and address these challenges, we interviewed 30 experts from a variety of disciplines to solicit their insights on the current status of HGE and its plausible futures. Interviews explored a range of themes encompassing history, technology, economics, ethics, perceptions of socio-cultural environment, and governance. Expert opinion converged around the effects of commercial interests in the research and development of HGE, the importance of soliciting publics' input, and the need to perfect the technology's safety and efficacy. Expert opinion diverged with respect to general attitude towards HGE, permissibility of germline editing, effects of HGE on healthcare systems, usefulness of the therapy-enhancement distinction, and whether scientists should self-govern their HGE use. Experts also noted current mechanisms for HGE governance and suggested novel means. Our discussion situates these insights in the greater historical context of emerging biotechnologies.

Expert Voices: Why Authority and Responsibility Matter in Human Genome Editing
Christopher Thomas Scott, Baylor College of Medicine; John P. Nelson, School for Future of Innovation in Society, Arizona State University; Haley Manley, Baylor College of Medicine; Cynthia Selin, Arizona State University; Stephanie Morain, Baylor College of Medicine

The future outcomes of human genome editing (HGE) research are highly uncertain, contingent upon the development of complex and variable biological, technological, economic, social, and political systems. At stake in exploring the future of human genome are questions about how responsibility and authority are distributed. Though we are not able to predict the evolution of human genome editing, we can systematically investigate questions about responsibility, authority and accountability in hopes of informing a more deliberate mode of governance. Rapidly emerging technologies demand novel approaches to governance and must necessarily begin by examining existing governance frameworks and asking questions about responsibility, authority, and accountability. Here, we report on one provocation that emerged from a coding exercise of semi-structured interviews conducted with a diverse group 30 HGE experts: How might authority and responsibility be distributed among researchers, funders, policymakers, and publics? We will examine one of the codes attached to this provocation, namely: Who is responsible for oversight and conduct of HGE? Analysis and first abstractions of the codes yielded three salient themes: 1) the role of scientists in HGE governance; 2) the stakeholders in a model of responsible governance and how should they be engaged; and finally, 3) whether governance can keep pace in an unregulated market.

Researching the Future: Scenarios to Explore the Future of

Gene Editing
Cynthia Selin, Arizona State University; Stephanie Morain, Baylor College of Medicine; Lauren Lambert, Arizona State University, School of Sustainability; John P. Nelson, School for Future of Innovation in Society, Arizona State University; Mahmud Farooque, Arizona State University Consortium for Science, Policy and Outcomes; Dorit Barlevy, Baylor College of Medicine; Haley Manley, Baylor College of Medicine; Christopher Thomas Scott, Baylor College of Medicine

Human gene editing technologies are but one constellation of emerging technologies that are sated with promises and perils, with new inventions and applications teetering into futures riddled with uncertainty. Better governance is needed in order to ensure that human gene editing serves yields positive societal outcomes. Scientific, policy, and ethics communities have recognized this necessity, but have demonstrated limited understanding of how to fulfill it. The field of bioethics has long attempted to grapple with the unintended consequences of emerging technologies, but too often such foresight has been isolated to single scholars making predictions or delivering cautionary tales. This research instead systematically reconfigures scenario planning, a tool developed in the high-stakes, uncertainty-ridden world of corporate strategy, for the equally high-stakes and uncertain world of the governance of emerging technologies. The scenario planning methodology is non-predictive, instead gathering a diverse array of perspectives to generate a spread of possible futures which diverge in their implications for different communities' needs, cares, and desires. In this article we relay how the scenario development process provides opportunities to reexamine and further understanding of the complex and dynamic systems which generate and shape new technologies. We detail a year-long scenario planning intervention that engaged experts from the biological sciences, bioethics, the social sciences, law, policy, private industry, and civic organizations. In addition to sharing the results of the study, we aim to advance anticipatory methods deployed in bioethics, demonstrating how this approach provides unique insights and helps to derive better research questions and policy strategies.

The Divide so Wide: Public Perspectives on the Role of Human Genome Editing in the Health Care System
David Tomblin, University of Maryland, College Park; John P. Nelson, School for Future of Innovation in Society, Arizona State University; Avery Barbera, Arizona State University; Melissa Smallwood, Arizona State University

Advocates of human genome editing (HGE) research routinely assert its potential to revolutionize medical treatment and produce widespread public benefits. Common within communities pushing for novel technological developments, these promissory visions - what Stephen Hilgartner calls "vanguard visions"—are routinely constructed without direct public consultation. This often leads to mismatches between technoscientific development and public priorities. To ascertain the potential for mismatch between HGE research and public priorities about health care innovation, we organized an open framing deliberative mapping exercise that situated HGE research in the broader context of the United States healthcare system. This exercise involved focus groups with 30 people from across the U.S. on two separate days. On day one, we asked participants to map a baseline of concerns about the healthcare system. On the second day, we introduced HGE as an innovation to improve medical treatments, mapped participant values regarding HGE, and asked them to prioritize HGE research relative to their overall concerns about the health care system. Almost across the board, participants felt that problems, such as the cost of health care and access to quality care should be addressed before HGE could be a meaningful treatment option. Many participants reported concern that HGE technologies might

amplify existing inequalities, rather than providing a means to solve them. We argue for the systematic use of open framing public engagement methods that situate emerging technologies in the broader context of the systems they will influence to reduce mismatches between expert and societal priorities.

Session Organizer:

Cynthia Selin, Arizona State University

052. Encounters with Failure in STS II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Science and Technology Studies has long focused on how knowledge is made and how publics are then enrolled in it. However, these past studies have often focused on successful articulations of knowledge; we argue that what is left behind, discarded or disputed is just as generative and important to research. While not exhaustive, these may include failures in policy, failures of pilot schemes or mundane failures in everyday life. Moreover, failure also occurs in relation to research processes. In research we can, for example, encounter absences in our data where perhaps we expected it to be. This can in turn make us unable to narrate and analyse the processes that enrol publics in the various failures that stand in relief to what becomes successful. What methods might exist or be developed to help discuss and analyse failure in the face of absent data, missing voices and actors for whatever reason we struggle to follow? This panel is primarily focused on the methods involved in researching failure or doing research in the face of failure or absence. As such, we invite papers that deal with one or both of these areas. We also welcome papers with a focus on digital methods or inventive methods. Due to the subject of the panel, we also encourage papers which reflect research projects at different stages of the research process. This panel aims to start and progress conversations amongst researchers about how conduct studies amongst failures and absences.

Participants:

Researching Significant Failure in Scientific Practice *Tobias Bernd Lehmann, TU Berlin; Michael Borggräfe, TU Berlin; Jochen Glaser, TU Berlin*

Failure – defined here as not achieving the goals researchers set themselves – has not yet been made an explicit topic by STS. Although failure surfaced in ethnographic studies of research, its role for the careers of researchers who failed or for the knowledge production of scientific communities has not yet been systematically investigated. Drawing on our project „Forms and Effects of Failure in Science“, we discuss theoretical and methodological challenges of defining failure in research practice and of empirically identifying cases of failure for study. The main obstacle to the study of failure and its consequences is the systematic underreporting of failure in publications, which makes it difficult to detect for community members, let alone outsiders. We discuss the following questions: 1) How to distinguish the kind of failure we are interested in - significant failure - from the everyday messiness of research practice? 2) How, by whom and under what circumstances is the outcome of a research project constructed as significant failure? And, pointing to the central risk of failure for our own research project: 3) How to empirically identify significant failure in scientific communities' discourses, given that reporting failure is systematically discouraged by the publication system? We discuss three approaches to identifying failure: screening journals for negative results; screening 'high risk, high reward' funding programmes; screening retraction notices for retractions due to honest errors. While these may enable the identification of significant failure, tracing the impact of failure in scientific communities remains difficult because failure is rarely talked about.

Time and Money: How Public Sector Agencies Resist Organizational Failure *danah boyd, Microsoft Research / Data & Society; Janet Vertesi, Princeton University*

This paper contributes to debates in the sociology of organizational failure by comparing the experiences of two

governmental organizations in the United States: the Census Bureau and the National Aeronautics and Space Administration (NASA). Prior studies of organizational failure typically focus on the private sector with its particular arrangement of funding and stakeholders; assume failure causes such as poor environmental fit or exogenous shocks to a company; and assert that failure or low reliability is unintentional and undesirable. Our ethnographic examination of two public sector, politically-imblicated sociotechnical systems reveals novel causes and roles for failure. We observed two resource-constrained arenas in which complex sociotechnical organizations confronted significant risks: the contemporaneous production of the 2020 census and the Europa Clipper Mission. Examining the dual roles of money and time as socially constructed, relationally invoked, and politically executed constraints upon local action, we observe how complex, tightly-coupled organizations of the type Perrow associates with failure deploy time and money as buffers against risk. We analyze how relationships are renegotiated alongside competing views of the organization's mandate, and how both time and money are co-constructed alongside powerful entities such as the Office of Management and Budget or Congress in addition to both internal and external stakeholders. Accounting for these socially-constructed "constraints" upon action enables us to articulate what actors do in contested terrain, to usefully reframe organizational failure for analysis, and to suggest implications for trust and legitimacy in public sector technical projects.

What glitches, accidents and breakdowns tell us about good relations between humans and robots *Chris Chesher, The University of Sydney; Justine Humphry, University of Sydney*

One way of understanding the good robot is by exploring how robots fail. Robot failure is endemic, as evident in the engineering measure 'mean time to failure'. Paying attention to failures as well as successes is a longstanding imperative in science and technology studies since the Strong Program and SCOT. In this paper, we analyse representations of failing robots in popular culture and draw on literature on glitches, accidents and breakdowns to make the argument that we can understand good relations with robotics and AI through their failures. Robotic malfunctions are commonplace in actual robots and in their fictional representations. The sentient robots in the TV series *Humans* and *Westworld Series 1* fail by becoming too human. Robots in *R.U.R.* and the *Terminator* franchise fail by turning on humans and trying to annihilate them. Failing robots feature in video memes featuring Robocup soccer players, DARPA challenge robots and Robot Wars. Experiencing robot failures can be highly affective, provoking frustration, anxiety or amusement. Breakdowns surface social expectations and political orders, providing potential impetuses for rearticulations (Honyg, 2016). They illustrate the fragility of actual robots, providing a counterbalance to the discourse of 'techno-hysteria' – technology out of human control (Leszczynski, 2019). They humanise the robot, showing they are subject to misfortunes just like ours. They can become a vehicle for new artistic practices (Menkman, 2011). In sum, they point us to potentially new knowledges, practices and methods for making 'good relations' with technology.

The Cycle of Doubt: how scientists perceive and address uncertainties and failures in data production *seokkyun woo, Georgia Institute of Technology; John Walsh, Georgia Tech*

Accelerating the pace of scientific discovery is of great interest to both natural and social scientists. With the advancement in robotics, machine learning, and artificial intelligence (AI), automation is being hailed as an unrivaled means to increase the pace of science. Yet, less attention has been given to the immense difficulties in producing data in many fields. The production of data is foundational, time-consuming, and highly problematic. In this sense, understanding how decisions are made when faced with data production failures, particularly how scientists use heuristics and learn from failures, can potentially

increase the pace of discovery. At the same time, analysis of such failures can provide important insights into the scientific process and the nature of learning in the social context of a scientific work setting. From ethnographic observations on data production failures in material science labs, we show how failures are perceived by scientists, the various solution searching strategies, and the conditions under which these strategies are used. Using Simon's problem-solving theory, we build from these in situ observations to construct a behavioral model of scientist's problem-solving strategy and discuss potential solutions to accelerate the pace of data production. The findings from data production failures have implications for ongoing debates on automation in science. While current discourse mainly focuses on the prediction aspects of AI, our findings from data production failures can suggest paths for improving learning from failures, applicable both to humans and machines, increasing the pace of science.

Session Organizer:

Katrine Meldgaard Kjær

Discussant:

Jessamy Perriam, IT University of Copenhagen

053. Epistemic Infrastructures - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Participants:

Fabricating governing panoramas? The SDGs as epistemic infrastructures *Sotiria Grek, The University of Edinburgh; Marlee Tichenor, University of Edinburgh; Justyna Bandola-Gill, University of Edinburgh*

Despite the multiplicity of actors, crises and fields of action, global public policy has known one constant: that is, the ubiquity of indicators in the production of governing knowledge. These measurements have become proxies for countries' general wellbeing and prosperity, and they have become the means by which different entities – multilateral and bilateral funding organisations, non-governmental and philanthropic organisations, and the countries themselves – make priorities about development investments and policy decisions both internationally and domestically. This paper will explore this phenomenon in the context of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) and their affiliated indicators, debated and introduced in 2015. The SDGs have not only sped up the process of the quantification of governance, but they have also led to new materialities, new interdependencies and new governing ideas that require innovative research and analysis. The paper will explore these interlinked processes and practices by offering a theorisation of SDGs as 'epistemic infrastructures'.

Epistemic infrastructure for local network connectivity *Caroline S Wagner, Ohio State University*

At the international level, scientific research and development operates as a network. Unless the project is highly formal, no international organization dictates who works with whom: the network of connections largely self-organizes in response to social, academic, and knowledge infrastructure incentives. As international cooperation has grown, we see many new actors developing capacity to participate. This dynamic has worked fairly well to grow capacity, although the rich continue to get richer even as new players join. The wealth of knowledge in the network is difficult to access for those at local levels. The system does very well in creating knowledge, but, without specific incentives, knowledge is not effectively distributed. The "local loop" in the global network is a significant challenge to governance, and one that needs more discussion. This presentation will consider possible methods of enriching the system by reaching the local level with scientific knowledge infrastructures.

Doing Human Rights as Indicators: Problematizing the Counting and "Cutting" of Social and Economic Rights *Josh Bowsheer, Brunel University London*

Since the early-1990s, a variety of social indicators have been proposed and utilised as a means of monitoring social and economic rights. Global indexes and indicator-based systems have subsequently proliferated both within global governance institutions and beyond, becoming the dominant way of 'doing' social and economic rights. Though existing scholarship has critiqued the ways indicators submerge important political questions about socioeconomic rights under technical questions about their measurement, there is less clarity about how the technics of indicators shapes our very understanding of those rights. Developing insights from Science and Technology Studies, this paper conceptualises socioeconomic rights indicators as information infrastructures, 'grey mediations' which configure the ways that the world can be seen, understood, and intervened in. Principally, the paper turns to Karen Barad's concept of 'cutting' to explore the ways that indicators parcel the world into discrete national units and, in doing so, constructs notions of agency that centre the state and its capacity to act within the limited parameters of national boundaries. The value of Barad's approach is that it demonstrates how practices of cutting make the world legible only at the expense of exclusions and thus draws critical attention to what has been excluded in the construction of indicators. Pursuing this trajectory, I suggest that socioeconomic rights indicators obfuscate the dynamic agency of the global economy and its uneven shaping of national spaces and capacities across North and South. Indicators, I conclude, provide ways of knowing the world that are antithetical to redistributive notions of global and postcolonial justice.

How numbers are made to count in energy policy *Susanne Jørgensen, Norwegian University Of Science And Technology,; Knut H Sørensen, NTNU Norwegian University of Science and Technology*

Quantitative information is important in the development of climate and energy policy, yet the additional work needed when providing such information to policymakers have received little attention by STS scholars. We call this type of work numeric work. Based on interviews with scientists that produce energy statistics and engage in modeling of energy production and use for policymaking, the paper aims to fill this gap by analysing the efforts of relevant calculation actors – what do they do to make numbers count? How are numbers produced and presented to become useful for policymakers? What activities are seen as necessary to create powerful and pervasive numbers? Trust in numbers is often believed to be produced through procedures and institutions that are seen to provide 'mechanical objectivity' what is seen to be based on strict quantification and scientific methods (Porter 1995). What is at stake here is what we may call the epistemic authority of quantitative information, a form of trust that may emanate from the producers' position in an institution and a scientific discipline. In line with other researchers (Rottenburg and Merry 2015; Sætman et al. 2011; Silvast et al. 2020) we show that mechanical objectivity may not always be enough, so additional work such as translation and articulation work are needed to provide epistemic authority to numbers. The paper contributes to STS literature by focusing on how scientific knowledge in the form of quantitative information is translated in policy contexts

The Making of Global Health Epistemic Infrastructures by and for Private Actors *Annabelle Littoz-Monnet*

This paper explores the role of private actors in the production of global metrics in health governance – with a specific focus on non-communicable diseases (NCDs) The global health metrics used in global health by the WHO, the World Bank or even global professional associations have been produced either for or by private actors. On the one hand, the WHO, concerned to

attract private investments and private funders, sustained a governance mode in which digital data and algorithms were mobilized in order to set priorities and calculate the impact of existing interventions and eventually showcase the benefits of 'investing' into NCDs. On the other hand, and because they also wanted to direct their own investments where most 'cost-effective', philanthropic players found the production of large datasets highly appealing and created 'data institutes' specifically designed to produce large data and estimates. These metrics and the models with which they have been 'calculated' has resulted in the production of NCDs as a technical, individual, biomedical and marketable problem.

Session Organizer:

Marlee Tichenor, University of Edinburgh

054. Global Health Futures and the Social Good II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:

Tigers on Safari: Asian Models for African Populations *Tyler Zoanni, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology*

In this paper, I focus on family planning and population control as one key arena where Asian pasts are being invoked to imagine the social good in African presents and futures. As many countries in sub-Saharan Africa are undergoing massive population growth, diverse actors including African states, NGOs, the IMF and the World Bank, and academic economists and demographers all assert that the demographic and economic transformations of the so-called "Asian tigers" can be successfully re-engineered in African contexts. This, in turn, is said to promise healthy and wealthy populations, defined by small families and highly skilled workers. Discussing examples from East/Central Africa, I show how family-planning interventions, demographic data-collection, and population policy-making draw upon Asian models. I also critically attend to some ways that these Asian models concretely do and not shape the actual provision of social services and health care on the ground. In this way, the paper uses a set of STS concerns (e.g., quantification and the performativity of economics) to reframe a classical anthropological conversation that compared analytic models for African and non-African societies. It does so by exploring comparison not simply as a research method but as a strategy central to contemporary governance and biopolitics at an emerging Asia-Africa nexus.

Global health reconfigurations at the interface between technoscience and finance *Roberta Raffaeta, Ca' Foscari University of Venice*

I propose to discuss an in-progress project that analyses the interfaces between technoscience and finance in the management of the COVID pandemic. Thanks to big data and AI, the interacting fields of One Health, postgenomics and data-centric epidemiology are offering paths to combine health and environmental data, promising to develop better health futures for both humans and non-humans. In this framework, the pandemic can be analysed as an ecosystemic assemblage produced by the merging of political regimes, social coordination, ecological conditions and bodily dispositions. My paper asks how this ecosystemic understanding of the Sars-CoV-2 virus, and its intersection with the moral turn in finance, may reshape global health. Both within finance and postgenomics there is a feeling of urgency and responsibility in addressing the socio-ecological crisis. Yet, both technoscience and finance are bounded to practices, epistemologies and systems of value that may jeopardize those progressive aspirations. My paper will explore these tensions, posing questions about which kind of socio-material relationships will be given value, cultivated and reproduced and how these will shape futures of health and care.

Entrepreneurship for the social good? Value conflicts in a

digital health project in India *Sandra Bärnreuther, University of Lucerne*

The provision of social services in India has changed significantly over the past decades. In the health sector, there is an increasing number of initiatives advocating entrepreneurial approaches. In this paper, I discuss the case of a social enterprise in Kolkata which, supported by the state government of West Bengal, is conducting a digital health project in rural areas based on an entrepreneurial model. The project promotes entrepreneurship as an effective means to deliver healthcare and also to provide professional opportunities for marginalized communities. The health workers employed in this project, however, are wary about this approach. In this paper, I trace the value conflicts that arose during the implementation process. I argue that they ensued from various understandings of what the social good means and I show how these understandings are connected to class and caste positions as well as distinct visions about the role of the state in providing social goods.

Session Organizers:

Sandra Bärnreuther, University of Lucerne

Ruth Prince, University of Oslo

055. Rethinking Outer Space And Science: Critical Engagements With The Cosmos And The Extra-terrestrial - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

Earthmoving for the Extraterrestrial: A Brief History of Cape Canaveral's Launch Complex *Jeffrey S Nesbit, Harvard University Graduate School of Design*

The American spaceport, and more importantly, its technical landscape, operate in the background for the technological and political progress in pursuit of the extraterrestrial. Throughout the construction of the launch complexes, earthmoving became standard practice to elevate rocket pads above sea level and protect against rocket blasts. However, a more extended history of earthmoving at Cape Canaveral curiously presents itself as an evolution of terrestrial form. The site was occupied by the native tribe Ais. Although known for being a nomadic community, made of "crude and flimsy" structures, Ais left behind burial mounds of built-up earth. A few of the burial mounds have been found in Kennedy Space Center. And still, earthmoving continues today. In 2016, an article advised the greatest threats to NASA's landscape are rising sea levels and hurricanes, causing substantial erosion to the beach, leaving active and historically significant launch facilities at risk. Cape Canaveral beaches are now preparing for additional dredging, importing new soil, and raising beach and dune elevations. This research of place-based science reveals a critical history of Cape Canaveral through an evolution of earthmoving practices, from cultural commemoration, extraterrestrial imagination and contemporary environmental crises.

"Canada's Spy-in-the-Sky": Peacekeeping Satellites and the Redefinition of Outer Space *Shannon Brown*

How was the "humanization of the universe" bound up with the production of relations between nations, and between private and public sectors within them, in the Cold War? This paper explores how these relationships were negotiated within Canada and subsequent attempts to extend them around the globe through United Nations forums. In response to the American Strategic Defense Initiative in the early 1980s, the Canadian state partnered with the country's burgeoning aerospace industry, law institutes, and peace activists to develop "the PAXSAT concept": a multilateral peacekeeping satellite system that used existing Canadian space infrastructure to monitor and verify arms control and disarmament agreements in space and on Earth, ending the superpower monopoly on verification. A technical design, a draft treaty, and a model world organization to manage PAXSAT and

its data each emerged out of this collaboration. These resisted American power in space and outlined a more inclusive approach to space governance, while also often reproducing global inequalities between stakeholders in outer space. In this paper, I draw together science and technology studies with Canadian international history and the history of neoliberalism to explore the political imaginations elaborated by PAXSAT as it was made, remade, and unmade over the course of the 1980s by both its Canadian creators and global representatives to the United Nations. Though it was never commissioned, in its promise to unite the Earth and orbit as a single sphere of activity PAXSAT offers us the opportunity to peer into the contested process of redefining humanity's relationship with outer space, whether through privatization or strengthening its status as a global commons. As concerns about the ongoing accessibility and security of outer space grow with the rise of megaconstellations and militarization, revisiting the longer history behind these contemporary debates allows us to understand the complexities of challenging and repairing unequal relations in orbit.

Mapping the Universe: Hubble and disembodied movement through time and space *Jessica Chapman, Carleton University*

Launched in 1990, the Hubble Telescope is responsible for much of what we know about our universe and the galaxies within it. Hubble's various missions gave us the first images of galaxies beyond our own – or so we think. The famous Hubble Ultra Deep Field is the deepest image of the universe that has ever been produced; however, it does not represent the universe as it existed in 2004 when the image was made. Rather, because of the time it takes for light from the distant universe to reach Hubble, it is a rendering of what the universe may have looked like only half a billion years after the Big Bang. Images generated by telescopes like Hubble are unstuck in both time and space – outdated temporally and recently rendered, they present us with the opportunity to move through deep space we could never experience first-hand. Exploration of deep space through mapping techniques like imaging and red/blueshift calculation allow us to experience space through mediated, disembodied forms of movement. As John Durham Peters (1999) argues, early transmission devices like the telegraph inspired disembodied communication achieved by, “the sharing of spiritual (electrical) fluids” (p. 139). Similarly, our technologically mediated pseudo-movement through deep space turns us into spirits from the future roaming distant galaxies. This paper explores the intimate sensory relationships we must form with technological processes in order to experience time and space beyond our embodied grasp.

Outer space, art and technoscience: Views from Mexico *Anne Warren Johnson, Universidad Iberoamericana Ciudad de Mexico*

In this paper, I reflect on Mexican discourses and practices of outer space exploration. I describe the ways in which participants in the Mexican space industry defend what they, repeating colonialist language, refer to as a “Mexican Conquest of Space”, appealing to the development of an “economic niche” in the commercialization of extraterrestrial resources, or the need to monitor terrestrial resources and environmental processes from outer space. I contrast the future imaginaries inspired by the possibilities of space technology with the more critical perspectives expressed by some Mexican artists, who celebrate the metaphorical possibilities of space exploration, while they argue for a radical reimagining of earthly relationality. The paper is part of an ongoing anthropological project about Mexican imaginaries of outer space that centers around ethnographic work with the Mexican Space Agency (AEM) and Kosmica, an international science and arts institute lead by a Mexican artist residing in Berlin. With this project, I hope to contribute to the ways in which STS generates dialogues between a wide variety of social actors and disciplines, as well as engage the social study

of outer space from a region that has been considered, at best, a peripheral participant in space exploration.

Astroprospecting: Accounting for “Place” in Space Science Infrastructure *Raquel Velho, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute*

With the collapse of the Arecibo observatory in the December of 2020, the outpouring of grief and loss that came from the online community showed that, more than a space of scientific importance, Arecibo held social significance to the island. However, it is becoming increasingly evident that we currently lack the conceptual and theoretical tools to account for the impact that scientific facilities have on a place as astronomy observatories are often contested spaces, such as the case of the Square Kilometer Array and the Thirty Meter Telescope. This paper will explore the limitations of existing literature in impact and assessment of research infrastructures, and will then propose a new conceptual-analytical framework to investigate the entanglements of astronomy research facilities with their localities. In asking, “How can we account for how astronomy clusters are entangled with their host communities?”, this paper proposes a conceptual framework that merges perspectives from feminist infrastructure studies and Latin American STS to redress existing gaps in research infrastructure literature without reducing hosting communities to their natural resources (clear skies, appropriate topography, etc.).

Session Organizers:

Julie Michelle Klinger, University of Delaware
Eleanor Armstrong, University of Delaware

056. The algorithmic turn of prediction - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Throughout history, the future has been an important reference for mankind. Its role for life in the present, however, has changed significantly in the course of time. While the future was initially found to be unalterable, with the development of modern societies it became to be understood as an open horizon that stands in a causal relationship to the present – the future got shapable according to actions and decisions in the present. This shift in terms of interpreting the future made it even more attractive than before to produce knowledge about it. Predictive strategies subsequently flourished and technologies thereby played an increasingly important role. With the advent of modern forms of algorithmic data analysis, with machine learning and artificial intelligence gaining center stage, another shift in referring to the future is likely, presenting an exciting as well as urgent challenge for social sciences in general and STS in particular. Before this backdrop, this panel aims to discuss the theoretical as well as empirical implications of algorithmic prediction in the datafied society. What effects does the algorithmization of prediction have on the systems, settings and situations concerned? How do algorithmic predictive technologies differ from their – allegedly less sophisticated – technological predecessors? And, last but not least, where are the analytical possibilities and limits of STS approaches regarding the algorithmic turn of prediction?

Participants:

The Algorithmic Reconfiguration of Decision-Making in Predictive Policing *Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld;*
Maximilian Heimstädt, Bielefeld University

Police organizations make decisions that have wide-ranging consequences for the freedom and behaviour of individuals. Today, such decisions are increasingly shaped by new data-centric technologies that aim at predicting criminal behaviour. In our paper, we investigate how decision-making processes in police organizations is reconfigured around new technologies of algorithmic forecast. For this purpose we identify and compare two generations of predictive policing software and show the different ways in which they reduce uncertainty in decision-making. We draw on interviews and observations conducted by the first author on an ongoing basis since 2017 in police organizations in Germany and Switzerland. While drawing mainly on the near repeat prediction pattern, assuming that

professional burglars act repetitively in narrowly defined temporal and spatial intervals, the first generation of police prediction software hardly corresponds to popular notions of big data analytics and a radical reconfiguration of police decision-making. Rather, the software mobilized only small amounts of data and produces forecasts not through algorithmic and inductive procedures but through a deductive and theory-driven extrapolation of past crime series into the future. However, a second generation of police forecasting software reconfigures the decision-making process in a much more fundamental way. The main structural principle of these new methods is a cross-database analysis platform, which allows the analysis of abundant and heterogeneous data sets. This in turn significantly reconfigures, as we will show in our paper, the process of future-related decision-making in police organizations.

Beyond The Prediction Paradigm. Challenges For AI In The Fight Against Organized/Infrastructural Crime *Paula Marie Helm, University of Tuebingen; Thilo Hagendorff, University of Tuebingen*

So-called predictive policing and pattern recognition technologies are already in use across many police departments. They are mostly focused on detecting and preventing overt (that is violent) and/or well-reported crimes such as burglary, robbery or theft. Organized crime, however, usually remains undetected. It is mostly based on corruption, collusion, money laundering, and complex global operations. Its infrastructural. Because of its complexity and the lack of data available, the development of AI-systems for criminal investigations in the area of organized crime is still in its infancy. However, there is reason to assume that sooner or later these technologies will also mature and be deployed. Like predictive policing and pattern recognition technologies, these systems raise ethical and epistemological concerns regarding the logic that is being applied, the data that is being used, the opacity of the systems, trade secrets, data protection issues and so forth. They therefore require closer examination from an ethical and critical perspective. This paper takes a first step in this direction by first identifying major points of criticisms already raised vis-à-vis existing policing systems and then taking a closer look at systems "in the making" that are aimed at more complex tasks, such as identifying, tracking and detecting infrastructures of organized crime. Finally, we summarize what it takes for machine learning-based policing to be "smart" in a comprehensive way that can overcome the limitations of the probabilistic logic of prediction.

Predicting children at risk: Controversial algorithms and infrastructural attachments *Helene Friis Ratner, Aarhus Univeristy; Kasper Trolle Elmholdt, Aalborg University*

In this paper, we explore how predictive algorithms in public administration become a matter of public concern, arguing that this is not only a matter of discursive articulations but also relates to what we term 'infrastructural attachments'. In developing this concept, we suggest that the public enactment of algorithms as controversial is contingent upon socio-material assemblages that become part of and are shaped by situated developments of algorithms. Building on interviews and document studies, we empirically compare two Danish local government experiments with algorithmic prediction of children at risk. The one experiment, 'Data-based early warning', was initiated by a municipality but was terminated in winter 2019 before the algorithm was put to use. The second and current experiment, 'Referrals in focus', is a collaboration between educational and research institutions and municipalities. Both experiments have become a matter of public controversy in Danish media. While the two cases are similar in terms of their aim and target group, predicting children at risk of lack of well-being and, ultimately, forcible removal from home, they also differ in their infrastructural set-up. These differences include which databases are connected in developing the algorithms, as well as the

institutional arrangements of their development, and they are critical to how the two algorithms become a matter of public concern. This testifies to the importance of scrutinizing the particularities of algorithmic controversies, and understanding algorithms as part of wider socio-material infrastructural arrangements rather than technical rationalities or computational formulas.

Session Organizers:

Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld
Maximilian Heimstädt, Bielefeld University

Chair:

Elena Esposito, Bielefeld University

057. Un/Making a Difference 1: materialities, textiles, making, mending & inventing

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Citizens with Secrets? How clothing inventors make extraordinary claims to ordinary rights and responsibilities *Kat Jungnickel, Goldsmiths, University of London*
Conventional governmental discourse links being a "good" citizen with transparency and visibility in the context of ever-increasing surveillance (Ball et al 2012). After all, as the saying goes, there's nothing to fear if you've nothing to hide. Here, transparency and visibility become logic for the construction of legitimate citizenship, which comes with associated rights and privileges. Yet there are other kinds of bodies, identities and practices that operate on the fringes of the normative visual "known", "transparent" and "good" citizen (Browne 2015; Dubrofsky and Magnet 2015; Kornstein 2019). This session excavates alternate expressions of citizenship outside this ever-watchful gaze in clothing form. Patent archives reveal a plethora of secret clothing inventions from mid nineteenth century to today. And, while much clothing literature explores garments for what they reveal - clothing can also conveniently conceal and conspire. Secret clothing patents examined in the ERC funded Politics of Patents research project include hidden pockets, convertible skirts and anti-harassment garments amongst others. These inventions materialise a multiplicity of critical concerns and creative, sometimes unexpected, responses from which we can ask: What is critical to keep private, hidden or protected from prying eyes? Who needs this more than others? Can the desire for concealment and secrecy be understood as acts of resistance against constant surveillance and tyranny of transparency? The many ways inventors have identified issues and sought to resolve them potentially reveals who has rights to privacy and secrets and who must make claims for them in alternate material and performative forms.

Choibá dolls: Material meanings that grow as they touch other bodies *Eliana Sanchez-Aldana, Universidad de Los Andes, Colombia*

Matholo, a UK based Afro-Southafrican weaver, takes the doll and looks at her for a while, a silent long while. She is visibly moved, not only by the quality of the stitches but by the doll itself. Doll in hand, she says: —This is the first time I've ever had a doll that looks like me—, as she combs her fingers through the braided hair of the small afro doll. Afro-Colombian women from the Artesanías Choibá collective make these dolls. These women's lives have been entangled with the Colombian armed conflict. Two decades ago, they had to leave their houses behind due to the forced displacement caused by the war. They now live in Quibdó (Chocó - Colombia). It was at this time that they started sewing these dolls as Christmas presents for their children because of the lack of other possible gifts. In our presentation, a conversation with members of the Choiba collective we will talk about the material meanings and the intangible bodies fabricated

when making these dolls. We will talk about how these material cultural experiences—these bodies, these corporealities (Foster, 1996)—, tell stories rarely told; how they produce a body—singular—that is multiple—plural— (Mol, 2002); how they have become both the/a voice and the/a livelihood that can respond to their everyday troubles.

Making Stories, Weaving Imaginaries, Mending Local Ecosystems *Marysol Ortega Pallanez, Carnegie Mellon University*

Narratives about the world design our worlds, shaping how we sense and act. In urban contexts, multiple dissonances exist between the narratives that make up a city's identity and the local ecosystem. In the desert city of Hermosillo, Mexico, a usually unnoticed dissonance is between the plants living in people's imaginaries of the city—often expressed through narratives of the quintessential Mexican garden—and what the territory can sustain. Though this might appear innocuous, it leads to serious consequences putting biodiversity at risk, jeopardizing the bioregion's resilience. This work comprises the materialization of personal everyday stories about city plants as expression of city's imaginaries; narratives become material through textile practices inspired by Mexican street embroidery. As dwellers of Hermosillo, we shared stories of our relations with plants from gardens, streets and local hiking trails. We are materializing stories by embroidering motifs and patterns that symbolize our encounters with the city's flora. Quotidian stories and their material manifestations may seem inconsequential in isolation. However, woven together, they uncover a patchwork of imaginaries. Thus, city dwellers delve into the tensions and relationality of local systems, opening the possibility to create new narratives toward a world-worth-living, in tune with the bioregion. The recursive nature of the imaginaries-material relation reproduces collective memories and systems of meaning, maintaining histories and making futures. Engaging with imaginaries through the material, embodiment and everyday narratives can open up spaces for STS to recognize the limits and excesses of science and technology in its interplay with socioecological spheres.

'Something New In Skirts': Fashionable Inventions For Female Shoplifters, 1880-1920 *Silvia Bombardini, Goldsmiths, University of London*

This paper investigates middle and upper-class women's shoplifting at the turn of the 20th century, in the Western world's first department stores. I frame this practice as a feminist act of resistance (Camhi 1993, Coulson 2013), parallel to the more high-profile suffrage protests at the time. Shoplifting is a mundane crime—'petty', by definition. Not despite but because of this, it prospered to the levels of what came to be known as a 'kleptomania epidemic'. I will argue that by way of shoplifting, women deviated from the path they were supposed to follow as consumers, to question 'from below' (Sheller 2012) both capitalism and the patriarchy: to question that is, the nature of ownership, of either objects or wives. From this theoretical starting point my presentation will focus on the clothes that shoplifters wore or might have worn, understood as sartorial technologies that enabled, facilitated, or encouraged theft as a creative act. More than just disguises, secret pockets, hollow heels, twice-lined petticoats and garters with hooks, would have been complicit in the shoplifter's crime. My research is conducted across archives, and I will present it by drawing visual and textual connections between the Politics of Patents (POP) dataset of clothing inventions, historical newspapers and criminal records recounting shoplifters' arrests. As is the case for women's inventions (Wajcman 2004; Jungnickel 2019), history forgets women's shoplifting when it's successful. My research is therefore necessarily speculative as well: drawing from the transcripts of those that failed, it seeks to reimagine successful thefts.

Transformational Creative Practices: Interventions Towards Sustainable Futures *Lara Houston, University of Sussex; Ann Light, University of Sussex; Kat Braybrooke, University of Sussex*

Due to ecological breakdown and the climate crisis we urgently need to find new ways of living within the earth's limits. In pilot research Light et al. (2018) find that creative practitioners—including artists, curators, designers and citizen-led collectives—are creating a range of transformative interventions that change participants' orientation to the world, their sense of agency and sense of potential. Creative practitioners are catalysing change by gathering publics around issues that matter to them in a variety of domains, and using a range of aesthetic, affect-driven, playful and participatory interventions that have multi-layered impacts across a range of scales. Our presentation explores the qualities of this category of 'transformative creative practice' (Light et al., 2018) and how these un/making practices contribute to the everyday acts of imagining and crafting arrangements for more liveable worlds. Despite reports of a 'crisis of imagination' in the stories we tell about climate change (Ghosh, 2016; Morton, 2013) our empirical work finds adaptive organisations, that are creating expanding and tentacular multi-layered practices that enrol multiple publics, often moving towards expanded imaginaries via mundane steps—engaging hesitancy, improvisation and speculation in compelling forms of 'material participation' (Marres, 2012).

Session Organizer:

Kat Jungnickel, Goldsmiths, University of London

058. Relations and Troubles of Tools of Valuation – II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

Research as Cashflow. Governance Effects of the Monetary Valuation of Academic Work *Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna*

Is the amount of money researchers acquire in competition with their peers an indicator of the quality of academic work? This remains controversial in both scientific communities and institutions. Nevertheless, in many contemporary national academic systems, the reforms of recent decades have made "third party income" an important indicator for assessing the performance of scientific institutions. In the spirit of neoliberal ideology, regulatory actors expect competition on the resulting quasi-markets to sharpen the profile of institutions and to increase the quality of the work of individual researcher. This paper will analyse the governance effects of this regime of valuing academic work. It builds on an analysis of the governance of research funding at Austrian universities, including interviews with presidents, deans and administrative staff. In terms of its main argument, the paper will trace how monetarization as an indicator for quality conflicts with other ways of valuing academic work within the institution. I will discuss how, at least in the Austrian context, seeing the performance of a university as constituted through its income in finite markets leads to institutional isomorphism rather than differentiation and profile building. And I will trace the deep ambivalences in how presidents and deans aim to manage the performance of scientists in this particular regime of valuing research.

Corals as Service Providers: Ecosystem Services and Value Relations Between Coral Scientists and Corals *Elis Jones*

In this paper, I examine and dissolve a tension visible in coral science valuation practices. Coral science is replete with appeals to the value of reefs. These appeals take many forms, including often a particularly economic one: claims about ecosystem goods and services (abbreviated to ecosystem services). For example, it is claimed that the various services provided by coral reefs per

hectare per year are worth \$352,249 (with several important caveats (Costanza et al., 2014)). Debates about ecosystem services often occupy extremes: to some, putting a monetary value on coral reefs is a pragmatic prerequisite to saving them. To others, it exemplifies the extractionist mentality which is driving the coral reef crisis in the first place. Despite this criticism, coral scientists regularly employ the language of ecosystem services, in both academic and public-facing outlets. Given that this is a discipline whose practitioners are famously affectively, socially and culturally connected to their objects of study (Braverman, 2018), this might seem odd: why should they utilise language which commoditises corals and reproduces the very kind of thinking which threatens them in the first place? Using an empirical grounding in interviews with coral scientists, and analysis of coral science documents, I argue here that the view of ecosystem services from within coral science is more nuanced than the two extreme points often found in ecosystem service debates. This points to new, more relational, ways to discuss the value of nature, which recognise economic importance of reefs but without being reducible to extractionism.

Exploring how Baltic Cod Modelling values Science with Mixed Methods *Judit Varga, Centre for Science & Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University; Jacqueline Ashkin, Center for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University, the Netherlands; Sarah de Rijcke, Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS)*

Quantitative modelling is a key tool of ordering and valuation in 'science based' fisheries management. Recent efforts to assess the Eastern Baltic Cod called for combining different modelling approaches: ecosystems and single species modelling. Using scientometrics, document analysis and interviews, we study how these modelling efforts value fisheries science and reflect on how combining methods shapes our analysis. Models are normative: they are co-produced with sciences' epistemic cultures; the politics of policies that call for and use them (cf. Leach & Scoones, 2013); and situated modelling practices (cf. Neff et al., 2017). Single species assessment models are popular in fisheries management, but EU and US policies have called for ecosystems-based approaches since the 2000s (De Santo, 2010; Quinn, 2003). The advice of ICES - an organisation providing 'science based' fisheries assessments - is key to European fisheries management. A 2020 ICES report calls for combining ecosystems considerations with single species assessment models to assess the Eastern Baltic Cod - a large and commercially significant stock said to be under threats that could be addressed through innovative modelling. Using scientometrics, we analyse publications about cod modelling. Scientometrics helps analyse large publication sets over time and varying scales, but often relies on aggregation and may reify analytical units. We also analyse ICES reports and interview scientists who perform ICES' cod modelling. These help study actors' values, but may over-emphasize the way ICES values fisheries science, obscuring alternative but relevant valuations. We explore how combining methods shapes our analysis of Baltic cod modelling.

Swipe Culture - Dating Apps and Valuation *Tilma* n Treier, Goethe University Frankfurt*

Location-aware dating apps like Tinder, Bumble or OkCupid are all the rage. Especially in a pandemic situation they represent important tools to virtually get in touch with other people by swiping through their profiles. In this paper I problematize valuation practices in the context of dating apps. Swiping as subjective articulation of desire is emblematic for that. Furthermore dating apps objectify these valuations in processes of abstraction and quantification exemplified by scoring techniques that facilitate the algorithmic sorting of profiles. As a consequence users face unequal connectivities depending not only on their societal positionality, but also on the technical configuration of the apps. This begs the question of whether the

socio-technical assemblages mediate a modification in the field of sexuality and love regarding the (economized) rationalization of desirability. By drawing on autoethnographic research on the dating apps Tinder and OkCupid I point to new modes of government of the self and subjectivities in relation to sexuality.

The Worth of a Stream *Hyojung Sun, Ulster University*

The music streaming's premium-based subscription model arose as an alternative to piracy, at a time when the recording industry struggled to valorise digitised music. The compromise price of a monthly fee £ (or €, \$) 10 for unlimited access to a global catalogue of music was born to suit two conflicting interests: major labels who wanted to charge as much as possible for music; and consumers, who once tasted free music, had lost their willingness to pay. Despite the growth of the streaming music economy, there are continuing concerns that the streaming model devalues the music. The current controversy around music value demonstrates the tension between the dematerialisation and the current mode of music commodification on the streaming platforms, triggering contestations of how music value is determined in the market and what makes music valuable. In times of quotidian ubiquity of music listening (Kassabian, 2013), what is the worth of a stream? Music valuation has so far followed 'uniform pricing' determined by the powerful market players and recording has been the primal form of music consumption for decades (Marshall, 2019) The neoclassical economy treats markets as concrete places where prices adjust to arrive at a competitive equilibrium between supply and demand (Milgrom and Roberts, 1992) and scarcely considers the changing dynamics. This article examines the current mode of calculative music commodification on the streaming platforms embedded in the economic markets (Callon, 1998; Callon and Muniesa, 2005). It explores the value judgment process that is complex and filled with power-laden political struggles (Fligstein, 1996) and uncovers the missing values in the process.

Wine Testing, beyond the Taste, What Values? *Helene Dodion, ULiège*

Little known for its wine, Wallonia has been trying to regain its historic brand image as a wine producer in recent years. In this trend, last autumn 2020, an independent laboratory was set up by wine-enthusiasts in order to offer an oenological advice and analysis service to Walloon winegrowers. In addition to aspects related to the consumable characteristics of the product, laboratory staff offer advice on improving the taste quality of the product. At the crossroads of valuation studies, ANT and sensory approaches, the researcher on board her bicycle along the Meuse-river, goes to meet the various actors involved in the wine production (winegrowers, consumers, supermarkets, hillsides, grounds, vine plant, barrel, meteorological elements...). She identifies the elements that put wine in tension as a taste product and the elements that influence its values. How to apprehend the gustatory quality of a wine according to the plurality of actors? How do the technologies offered by this laboratory bring these multiple values into tension? What does the sensory approach say about Wallonia as a wine-producing territory? There are the questions this paper will try to answer.

Session Organizers:

Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech
Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna

Chair:

Kristin Asdal, TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture

059. Seeds for a Planthropocene: Growing Good Relations among Plants and People I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

If the Anthropocene is a bad scene that grows capital and conquest, and stages unlivable relations among people and more-than-human kin, what

methods, modes of attention, and tactics do we need to stage relations otherwise? Can we learn to grow solidarities rather than disparities? This double panel explores ways that people stage relations with plants in order to offer generative grounds for reimagining the relations that can grow livable worlds. The papers speculate on ways of seeding Planthroposcenes, that is, activating scenes in which people form solidarities with plants as a means to seed good relations. Planthropocene thinking, which displaces the self-aggrandizing human, and centres a collective, hybrid entity composed of plants and people, attunes us to forms of growth that are not about growing markets or expanding capitalist production. As artists, practitioners and researchers we weave together stories about plants and people from the Global North and South, engaging anticolonial and decolonial frameworks to reckon with ways of doing plant/people relations differently. The papers explore the promises portended by vegetally-engulfed ruins in Cambodia, resistances to the toxic foundations of green development in Mauritius, the activist artworks of the Lawn (Re)Disturbance Laboratory in NY, a vegetable patch on stolen land in Toronto, efforts in feral viticulture to re-wild grapes, a praxis for attuning our feral bodies to plants and fungi, practices that support artists' dialogues with plants, plant/people intimacies among Indigenous elders and their allies in South Africa, and the unseen relations of seeds in the wake of seed monopolies.

Participants:

Feral Viticulture: Experiments in Re-Wilding Wine Grapes

Deborah Heath, Lewis and Clark College

Grape vines have been cultivated, and their fruit fermented, for thousands of years. Notable travelling companions of Roman and European imperial expansion, these deep-rooted perennials have also travelled far and wide along with human traders, missionaries, and settler-colonists. Since at least Roman times, grape vines have been propagated asexually, through cuttings, each cutting yielding a genetic clone of the parent plant. Along with other technologies of control and exclusion, from the trend towards monoculture to the appellation schema favoring a short list of "noble grapes" among the thousands of extant wine grapes, this has stifled the range of viticultural biodiversity. So has the predominance of chemical intensive agricultural practices, the use of herbicides, pesticides, and other synthetic additives, which have suppressed the lively array of soil microorganisms that otherwise collaborate with the roots of vines to enhance a vibrant subterranean multispecies microbiome. The three US west coast vintners presented in this paper aspire to grow grapes otherwise. One farms a feral vineyard abandoned for sixty years, located on a Native American reservation, filled with hybrids emerging from grapes having sex. Another grows both grape vines and rootstock from seed, aiming to encourage crosses producing unique new varieties, perhaps resistant to climate change. The third nurtures a polycultural multispecies site with livestock, a forest garden, and over 100 grape varieties encouraged to commingle and mutate. Each of these enterprises embraces serendipity and its potential for sustained vitality in the borderlands where wild, feral, and cultivated intersect.

The feral body, a tool of radical dialogue with plants and fungi

Claire Loussouarn, Goldsmiths College, University of London

Anthropocene thinking with its narrative of agency and independence is perpetuating the idea that as humans we have gained evolutionary mastery over other species and that therefore we alone have the solution to our misery. Against this one-sided self-absorbed narrative, criticisms especially among feminists (Haraway 2016, Grusin 2017) and anthropologists (Tsing, Swanson, Gan, Bubandt, 2017, Myers 2018), reveal how malleable, relational, multiple and interpedently tied to others species we actually are. Joining forces with these voices, this paper proposes to turn to our moving bodies to seed a new type of relationship between people and plants/fungi. Through an examination of my movement practice mixing eco-somatics, meditation and insight herbalism, I will explore how to enter in

dialogue with plants and fungi by letting our feral side unfurl through layers of conditioning and by nurturing kinesthetic and ecological awareness. By acknowledging and using the moving body as a tool and mode of thinking in its own right, my practice responds to previous calls for postanthropocentric and innovative ways of thinking which break away from the assumption of human uniqueness (Braidotti 2017) and for 'stag[ing] new scenes and new ways to see and seed plant/people relations in the here and now' (Myers 2018: 4).

How visual artists engage plants in non-verbal dialogues

Kenneth Chau

A recent resurgence within contemporary art explores the meeting point between plants, people and power, especially the power imbalance between the human world and their non-human counterparts. This paper explores a range of artists' efforts to change the nature of plant/people relations through their efforts to communicate with plants. Looking to contemporary artistic practices involving non-verbal dialogue with plants, I engage with artistic practice as a medium, one that establishes a proactive platform or foundation for staging relationships between humans and plants, relations that would be unimaginable in a scientific laboratory. As STS scholars and anthropologists extend their methods beyond the human (Kohn, 2013; Helmreich, 2009), it is also important to explore the parameters of our communication with more-than-human non-humans in visual art. How do artists understand plants and communicate with them? Can we understand the world from a plant's perspective? What kinds of conversations between plants and people are possible? What kind of shift in perception would be necessary to form solidarities with the plants and grow a Planthroposcene (Myers, 2018)? In this talk I document my own artistic practices engaging in plant communication alongside works by other artists developing creative means to connect empathetically with plants. I offer an ethnographic and artistic reflection on non-verbal dialogue with plants, engaging the artworks as encounters that bridge the gaps in communication between people and plants.

Involuntary methods in a forage reserve: walking, talking, and picturing plant/people intimacies

Denisha Anand, Princess Vlei Forum

My first visit to Leliefontein, 'Lillyfountain' commons in South Africa was in 2013 as a graduate student in plant biology. My experiences harvesting Acacia karoo for chemical analysis in this forage reserve propelled my transition from science to the arts. I share ancestry with people of this region and this involves me deeply in the intimacies of the land and her bodies. Despite violent colonial narratives implying misuse and overgrazing, traditional land use and relations in Leliefontein are centred around care and working-with the rich Indigenous plant diversity of the Succulent Karoo biome. These forms of care and intimate engagement with plants, people and land are seeded from ancient practices of the Khoe and San ancestors of the people living in Leliefontein today. To draw out these stories I develop involuntary methods to explore interspecies relationality in conversation with feminist theories of affect and ethics of response-ability (Hustak & Myers, Haraway). Working with elders, children, sakmanne, gardeners, herders and bossiedokters, I adapt participatory action research methods including photo voice and transect walks, to engage plant practitioners and their diverse intimacies. Images and walks activate stories of the spiritual, symbolic and medicinal properties of plants. As I move through a range of sites, from open mountain ranges, to soup kitchen vegetable gardens, walks through this landscape are the catalyst for storytelling about these deep plant/human involutions.

Seeing the unseen in seeds

Zayaan Khan, Zayaan Khan

Seed is highly contentious in the current political climate, with agribusiness oligarchs, governments, world organisations and

breeders all vying to patent seed within a privatized system, valorizing one kind of seed over another. In this talk I distinguish seed that is seen versus seed that is unseen, that which is not patented or corporatized and thus not recognized. Corporate seed has gripped the attention of global governments as part of a scheme to support food security, using seed laws to control the sale and distribution of these seeds and seed companies, affecting import laws of each country signing on to these agendas. Seen seed becomes a commodity separate and unseen seed, including seeds that do not conform to patent standards, seeds whose genetic material dance along ancestral lineage, easily morphing or more easily adapting to changing environmental conditions or desires, appear to vanish. How do seeds become essentially invisible, and by extension their human relations too? Unseen seed is the seed of the global peasants, gardeners, heirloom seed revivalists, seed jewelers and wild musicians, it is the seed of unsettled harmony connected to origin stories and ancient recipes. This seed relies on intimate relations of care. Seed is culture, linked so closely with origin stories, Indigenous cosmologies, caregivers recipes built by generations of care with the soils and waters and insects. This relationship is ancient and at great risk of being silenced into extinction. This paper traces some seed stories in the face of oppressive seed laws in South Africa.

Session Organizer:

Natasha Myers, York University

Chair:

Natasha Myers, York University

Discussant:

Banu Subramaniam, University of Massachusetts Amherst

060. (Re)configuring care practices in pandemic times II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Care practices were addressed in STS by Annemarie Mol (2002, 2008, 2010) as capturing a specific way of engaging with material reality as well as framing situated human relations. Hence, care bears not only upon intimacy or affectivity, but relates to forms of interdependency between ontology and normativity (“ontonorms”; Mol 2012). The session starts from and further develops the discussions on relevance of care practices focussing on the (re)configurations of care practices during the COVID-19 pandemic. Such a discussion of „care“ takes up not only a currently highly relevant social topic, but also acknowledges the salient empirical shaping of theoretical reflections on care in STS as ways of handling reality and transforming social relations. While COVID-19 differently addresses virologists, clinicians, physicists, epidemiologists, immunologists, or economics (Mol and Hardon 2020), a wide range of practices of care proliferated in response to the health crisis beyond these formal and mainstream settings, draw mainly on spatial (and social) proximity (neighbourhoods, peer-groups), and emphasised a temporal continuity of the caring engagement (regular visits, extended homeschooling). In a word: specific (re)configurations of care are rendered visible in dealing with personal concern, vulnerability, and (inter)dependence (Kittay 2015). The session includes contributions on: – expertise negotiated along care practices; – care related to groups traditionally framed as disadvantaged: elderly, people with disabilities, indigenous people, and other culturally diverse groups; – goods shaping actors understanding of care; – alliances of human and non-human entities as modes of pragmatic coping with pandemic crisis; – methodological adjustments regarding (re)configurations of care.

Participants:

Being (un)observable: Client/Provider Power Dynamics In Home Visitation Programs During COVID-19 *Kim Sigmund*, University of Amsterdam - AISSR

Home Visitation programs have spread prolifically across Los Angeles, USA in recent years. Part of the public health system, these programs offer “at-risk” mothers parenting support, guidance, and access to resources with the goals of limiting

instances of child abuse, assisting with child development, and helping to build and maintain familial ties. The core of these programs are the home visits, in which a trained Home Visitor enters the family home in order to observe mother-child interactions and to regularly assess the mother’s level of psychological risk and the child’s development level. However, at the onset of the COVID-19 pandemic, in-home visits became experimental interventions as programs moved to virtual visitation services. With this step, the adoption of new forms of technology shifted the methods of engagement between parents and Home Visitors, mediated new power relations in the political economy of care, and led to a lopsided biotechnical embrace (Good, 2001) of video-based telehealth systems. Using data gathered from ethnographic interviews, I will discuss how the technological shift in home visitation programs has given mothers the agency to shape their own program experiences by allowing them to choose when to be (un)observable through a digital device. This power shift in the ability to control visibility directly contradicts the purpose of home visitation programs to observe and educate mothers, calls into question how the benefits of virtual home visitation systems can be evidenced, and speaks to the ways in which virtual technologies currently mediate power relations in American health-based settings.

How to diagnose at distance? A study on the use of telemedicine in times of crisis *Alexandre MATHIEU-FRITZ*, University of Gustave Eiffel; *Dilara Vanessa TRUPIA*, Inserm

Since the 1980s, telemedicine has developed very slowly and unevenly in France. It was not until the SARS-COV-2 pandemic that it became a major part of the daily work of healthcare organizations. If, until 2020, teleconsultations (TLCs) represented less than 1% of consultations reimbursed by French healthcare system, this number went from 60,000 TLCs (in one year) in September 2019 to 4.5 million (in one month) in April 2020 alone (ie. 28% of consultations). These figures allow us to grasp the extent of the phenomenon. However, they do not provide insight into what happens concretely during these consultations whose remote reconfiguration is by no means straightforward. This proposal presents the findings of two empirical studies conducted simultaneously through semi-structured interviews with two different groups of practitioners, hospital-based dermatologists and general practitioners, on their use of TLC in times of crisis. These practitioners must both ensure continuity in the care of their regular patients, while also managing and referring new patients suspected of having contracted Covid-19 through TLC. This proposal reports on the concrete modalities through which care practices are (re)configured at distance, as new forms of proximity are established in the context of the health crisis where remoteness takes on quite singular meanings for each. This proposal contributes to the field of STS by presenting the study of the concrete efforts to make remote care work, as a way of understanding the broader routinization process of telemedicine and to report subsequently on the major transformations of care practices.

“My Student is A Supernova” —Teaching and Care in the Digital K-12 Classroom during the pandemic. *Nadine Tania*, University of California, Irvine; *Fred Ariel Hernandez*, UCLA

In this presentation we share results from a community participatory research project examining emerging and adaptive care practices within two K-12 schools located in the San Gabriel Valley of Southern California. Our study examines how schools imagine and attend to the “well-cared for” student. Despite widespread deficit perspectives on K-12 education, the pandemic has highlighted the ways in which local schools are essential actors woven into the fabric of neighborhood life. Covid-19 protocols required teachers to reinvent classroom teaching and

caring practices for the digital classroom with mixed results. At the same time, schools emerged as sites providing a multitude of “wrap-around” services tackling issues such as food insecurity, the digital divide, access to public health and safety information and resources. We examine the materiality of care and its (re)configuration during the pandemic, its effects and disruptions to schools’ spatial practices, student accommodations, social engagements in classrooms, teacher interactions, and surveillance activities. Through remote interviews with teachers and administrators, supplemented by remote data collection focused on publicly available communication (print, digital, and social media, school websites, curriculum schedules, and recorded public broadcasts of school board meetings), and semi-private communication within school communities, our findings reveal the adaptive care strategies schools and teacher enact even as the pandemic exacerbates disparities between independent (private) schools and public schools, students and families during a year when “learning loss” is an anticipated outcome of across K-12 education researchers, teachers and administrators (NAED, 2020)

The Paradox of Access: Information Access for Deaf Jordanians in Pandemic Times *Timothy Y. Loh, Massachusetts Institute for Technology (MIT)*

During the COVID-19 pandemic, a common experience of many deaf communities around the world was delayed access to urgent information. In response, the focus in a number of information access Facebook groups shifted to providing information about the virus. In these groups, deaf people can request for certain items to be interpreted and volunteers can take on those assignments to provide access to that information. While such grassroots efforts are laudable, this paper draws upon data from such a Facebook group based in Jordan to explore the difficulties that might arise in such situations through a lens of disability justice (Piepzn-Samarasinha 2018; Ginsburg et al. 2020). This critique first recognizes that such information gaps should not exist and information access would ideally be provided by the state. This critique also builds on the longstanding work by Deaf studies scholars and sociolinguists about the ways interpreters can disempower communities (Davidson 2000; Campbell et al. 2008; Caselli et al. 2020); in this case I examine how such efforts might be counterproductive when volunteers are new to the community and language or are otherwise not well-trained, especially in the Jordanian context where sign language interpreting standards have yet to be established (Hendriks 2008). For instance, they might take attention off the deaf community onto themselves, and to receive praise for volunteering as interpreters whether they do so effectively or not. This paper calls for a critical rethinking of how such “care” efforts can be configured to be more empowering of disadvantaged communities.

Session Organizer:

Stefan Nicolae, University of Trier

Discussant:

Cristina Popescu, EHESS - Centre d'Etude des Mouvements Sociaux

061. Doing and Making Times II: Speeds

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Participants:

Sociotechnical deadlock: overlapping time tenses in digitalization processes *Alin Ake-kob, Nord University; Roger Andre Søraa, NTNU*

How do time tenses of past, present, and future overlap in digitalization processes in organizations? The concept sociotechnical change prompt us to think about time tenses in technological endeavors as moments with clear boundaries – where past technology is replaced with contemporary ones, and where future technology is imagined to replace the present

technology and practices. In this paper we challenge this view by pointing out how time tenses can overlap during digitalization projects. We introduce the concept “sociotechnical deadlock” to define the moments during technological projects where time tenses overlap and become entangled. Through an empirical study based on participatory observational fieldwork as an assistant in a Norwegian care facility complemented with interviews to healthcare professionals, we analyze how time tenses materialize and are practiced during digitalization processes in organizations. The ethnographic methods combining participant observation, interviews, and documents, allowed us to identify situational patterns, and through the analysis of these situations this paper empirically supports a material and phenomenological understanding of time. We advance the STS argument that time tenses are socially constructed to argue that they are defined through practices and through objects and technologies used in the production of socio-technical assemblages. Our key contribution is that time tenses can overlap through the coexistence of objects and technologies in digitalization projects, thus highlighting the synesthetic as well as the tangible character of time.

Temporalities of non-knowledge production. Acceleration and repetition in the Italian asylum system. *Lorenzo Olivieri, University of Bologna*

Attempts to govern and control the movement of people across borders are shaped by temporal demands. More specifically, speed and acceleration are increasingly pursued as means for alleviating, and possibly overcoming, time-wasting and repetition in practices of border control. At the same time, however, population mobility depends on the incessant production of knowledge about border-crossers. What is the relation between acceleration and knowledge production and what are the consequences of this pursuit for acceleration in population mobility? I suggest that this struggle for acceleration in practices of population management tends to produce non-knowledge about people who resort to non-linear, alternative temporal trajectories. I illustrate this tendency by analyzing the case of the Italian asylum system, which has recently introduced so-called accelerated procedures to streamline the asylum process. These procedures apply, for instance, to people of certain nationalities as well as to those who reiterate their asylum application. These applicants have less time to prepare their cases, to provide relevant evidence and to appeal in case of a negative result. As a consequence, a thorough assessment of their cases is not carried out and knowledge about them is willingly not (or partially) produced in order to speed up the process of decision. This work is part of the ERC-funded “Processing Citizenship” project and it relies on interviews and textual analysis of Italian regulations. It aims to contribute to STS scholarship by stressing the connection between knowledge production about population, time, and power relations.

When the World Comes to an End: An Ethnography of Temporal Partialities *Tomás José Usón Pizarro, Humboldt University of Berlin*

When hearing stories about the past and anticipations of the future, we tend to think about narrations that are self-contained; in other words, tales that are sustained through a coherent presentation of the temporal moments they want to depict. But these narrations are never complete; instead, they are commonly portrayed as fragments of a major history. This tension between the whole and the part, i.e. the duration that makes sense of a moment and the instant that brings duration into life, has been the center of vigorous debates about the ontological condition of time – from Bergson's notion of duration and Bachelard's revindication of the instant to current discussions of anthropological presentism and historicism. In this paper, I overcome the duration-instant dichotomy and move from an essentializing to an assemblage-oriented understanding of time. Reflecting on Strathern's Partial Connections and Haraway's

Cyborg Manifesto, I explore how connections among different versions of the past and future occur, even after the worlds that make sense of those temporal stages have been destroyed. I take as a case study my ethnographic work in Ancash, a region in Peru that has faced several extreme events in the last century – including the 1970 earthquake that annihilated cities like Yungay and Huaraz, forcing their inhabitants to start from scratch. By focusing on their survival stories and narrations about the worlds that disappeared, I invert Strathern's proposal to explore the partialities that, beyond connecting, can also detach when dealing with narrations of destroyed pasts, cracked presents, and uncertain futures.

Of Timekeepers and Proteins: How International Time Standards Co-Shape 3D Molecular Cinema *Filip Vostal, Institute of Philosophy of the Czech Academy of Sciences*

It is only recently that visual representation of biological processes taking place on sub-atomic, atomic, molecular have been “brought to the lab” so that such resolutions became visible to human eye. This paper focuses on the latest iteration in these developments: 3D molecular cinema. Namely it investigates how molecular dynamics gets “arrested” by the use of femtosecond pulses, and subsequently translated into a different time-resolution by using x-ray free electron lasers and attendant methods. The main argument of the paper is that representation of scientific practice has largely disregarded temporal underpinnings, namely how the second that make visualization of knowledge claims by using 3D molecular cinema possible due to the international time standards, atomic frequency time standards, and the maintenance of the second by the International Bureau of Weights and Measures (BIPM). The paper thus offers two contributions. First, more generally, it suggests that capturing molecular dynamics – particularly structure, behaviour and un/mis/folding of protein molecules – into cognitive digestibles is not a frequent theme in STS-oriented studies of “molecular life.” Second, more specifically, studies in science representation and visualization, and their explanatory potential, would benefit from a further interaction with social studies of time, particularly how planetary time-keeping units are performed, measured, and maintained.

Session Organizer:

Helge Jordheim, University of Oslo

Chair:

Helge Jordheim, University of Oslo

062. Being a Lab, Studying a Lab: Practicing Good Relations in Building Qualitative Research Infrastructures - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Critical STS scholars have exposed “lab life” as a key arena of agentive relations and as sites of more than technical assemblages (Clark and Fujimura 1992, Traweek 1998). Social scientists have also found the form of “a lab” generative for organizing collaborations and essential to gaining institutional recognition and funding. We seek to move beyond the important work of first generation lab studies that demonstrated the political nature of (bench and social) science to place the studying of labs alongside the establishment of qualitative STS labs-- ones that draw on traditional laboratory models yet incorporate alternative frameworks of inclusion and non-extractive epistemologies. Our focus is this dual nature of labs as systems of relations. Extending Roy's (2018) incitement for feminist laboratory methods into the work of qualitative labs, we ask two central questions: what makes a qualitative lab a lab, and what are its methods of good relations? Following Liboiron et al. (2017), how do labs relate to, or materialize in, particular methodologies, ethnographic productions and collaborations?

Participants:

The Transformation of Academic Labs in the Biomedical Sciences: Funding and the Emergence of Larger Labs in the Era of Commercialization *Annalisa Saloni, Independent*

Scholar, formerly University of Pennsylvania

Concerns about the influence of increasing commercialization of research on university-based research in the life sciences have primarily focused on new corporate practices by academic scientists, as well as the influence of this phenomenon on research agendas and content of published research. The organization of academic labs in this area was assumed by policymakers and STS scholars alike to have remained essentially unchanged during this period. This paper examines an episode challenging that assumption: the emergence of larger lab groups in the biomedical sciences. Through changes in practice, the analysis shows how, in the case of Canada, key changes in funding practices in biomedical research beginning in the mid-1980s led professors to adopt new work and organizing practices. Based on evidence from work history interviews with older and retired professors done during a larger ethnographic study of academic labs, the main argument is that the mid-1980s are a key turning point in the social organization of academic labs in the biomedical sciences, where new practices began which reallocated funding to more productive researchers led to a transformation of the social organization of work in this field, including institutionalizing a new role for the researcher and giving rise to larger hierarchically-organized labs. The study shows how a practice-based approach can be used to examine the relationship between changes at the lab level and the broader institutional environment, and brings lab studies into conversation with the growing literature on political economy of research.

Qualitative Labs in Relation to Physical Science Infrastructures:

Integrating and Archiving Disaster Data *Jennifer J Henderson, Texas Tech University*

What counts as a lab—or whether we ought to duplicate the “lab” concept in STS—are questions I have asked myself over the past four years as a qualitative research scientist in a federal lab and now as new faculty in a geosciences department. Feminist and postcolonial scholars advocate alternative lab practices, such as those that flatten hierarchies, foreground equity, and anchor science in “specific places, complex local traditions, ethics, contexts and research questions” (Liboiron & Molloy 2017). This presentation follows this trajectory to map relations between quantitative and qualitative researchers in West Texas engaged in building a regional infrastructure to collect, archive, and integrate continuous data about the atmosphere, people, and the environment--what I call the atmo-bio-eco-sociality (after Rose 2021) of disaster. The infrastructure aims to improve experts’ (and nominally the community’s) ability to help others survive weather and climate hazards. Here I ask, what is “integration” or “archive” or “improve”? How might these concepts be deployed to theorize the research spaces and temporalities needed to detect, prevent, and mitigate harm? To identify missing relations? This presentation also asks about motives and interests, the framings of relations relative to the university, grant agencies, students, tenure itself--and the relations between the individual labs that are networked in this endeavor. Where positivist framings of solvable problems, big data, and generalizable findings—among other troubles—dominate much of the discourse about disaster research, how do qualitative researchers situate themselves among and build “good” socio-material relations with others?

The Bricolage in Digital Social Research: An Ethnography of Media Labs *Marta Severo, University Paris Nanterre*

Based on the experience of the MIT Media Lab, many universities have opened structures, usually called “media lab” (Venturini et al. 2017), studying social phenomena through digital social research. Their analyses are generally supported with Internet data that are perceived as real-time traces of social action and which can provide answers also in real time. Within the framework of this research, a rapid workflow has been established, which is organized in three phases: data collection,

data analysis generally based on quantitative “black box” methodologies (Latour 1987) and their interpretation usually based on visual representations. Often this research takes the form of “data sprint”, i.e. intensive work over a short period of an interdisciplinary team around preselected digital datasets (Berry et al. 2015). This communication aims at studying the role of bricolage (Lévis-Strauss 1966; Certeau 1990; Denzin, Yvonna 1999), as an approach to qualitative inquiry, in these labs and more generally in STS. We argue that in these centres, the bricolage, i.e. the qualitative development of eclectic multi-theoretical and multi-methodological approaches, is essential to meaning-making in research. We will present the first results of an analysis of 9 media lab (in Europe and the US). The analysis, based on in-depth interviews and on the study of the scientific production and of the communication through websites and social media, focuses on the: organization of the physical space; organization of the team; gender balance; organization of the research workflow; balance between theory, data, methods and tools; and the use of the term “bricolage”.

The Impact of Mobility on Researchers' Collaborations in a Developing Country: The Case of Turkey *Gökçe Nuhoglu, Middle East Technical University; Arsev Umur Aydinoglu, Middle East Technical University*

High Performance Computing (HPC) meets the high computational needs of researchers dealing with big data. This sophisticated computation environment is for researchers looking for solutions to complex questions. Collaboration is common in accessing advanced equipment, and the literature on the international big data collaborations of researchers is quite rich. However, there is limited literature searching specifically for the international collaboration of researchers using HPC. In this study, we investigate researchers affiliated with Turkish universities and using HPC regarding collaboration. We generate data through semi-structured interviews that are conducted with researchers in Turkey using HPC. The findings of the study show that international collaboration is a need for researchers in Turkey to reach advanced equipment as there are not many in the country. Thus, network connections are vital for collaborations; however, researchers' poor mobility is a barrier to expanding these networks and building trust to collaborate. Although science is a collaborative effort, it is not easy for researchers in developing countries as they are not generally part of the global research communities and collaborations. Consequently, researchers using HPC in Turkey cannot collaborate due to poor mobility and have difficulty in accessing the required equipment for their research. Our results present the effect of mobility on the motivations of international collaborations established to access specialized equipment.

Session Organizer:

Rebecca Howes-Mischel, James Madison University,
Department of Sociology and Anthropology

Chair:

Megan Tracy, James Madison University

Discussant:

Rebecca Howes-Mischel, James Madison University,
Department of Sociology and Anthropology

063. Cannabis knowledges: research, regulation practices and implications - II: Regulations, activism and knowledge production

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Participants:

Activism and Expertise in Cannabis' Regulation in Argentina
Oscar Eduardo Aguilar, CONICET - Instituto de Estudios sobre la Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad Nacional de Quilmes; Maria Cecilia Diaz, Instituto de Humanidades,

Universidad Nacional de Córdoba (IdH-UNC); Lucia Ana Romero, CONICET - Instituto de Estudios sobre la Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad Nacional de Quilmes

This paper discusses the role of activism and expertise in the recent regulatory process of cannabis in Argentina, exploring the participation and engaging of citizens in science and public policies. We assume that the recent cannabis regulation in Argentina emerges from a bottom-up mobilization of different types of knowledge, expertise and collective actions from civil society toward local politicians and other forms of government administrators. Based on ethnographic fieldwork (including in-depth interviews and document analysis) we identify three momentums of the regulation, displaying varied arrangements or interplays of expertise (citizen knowledge, technical/scientific/medical, political, legal), activisms (individual, collective) and advocacies (political, scientific), and so the conformation of hybrid networks. In an early local-scale dynamic (2012-2015), medical experts allied with singular activists, growers' organizations, and some local administrations to promote medical uses of cannabis and new local political initiatives. Later, at the national level (2016), renewed forms of cannabis activism, mainly organizations of families and children users of cannabis, gained attention of the public sphere, reaching out new political and expert alliances (i.e. National Cannabis Law of 2017) and spreading their form of organization across the country. Recently (2019-present), a new wave of regulations built-in-local have been taking place trying to adapt the national policy to municipal configurations of actors, deploying new local agreements such as collective and cooperative cultivation, new parliamentary projects regulating industrial exploitation of medical cannabis and different hemp industries. Through a detailed description of these moments, our objective is to analyze the particularities of cannabis regulation in Argentina.

Cannabis and Experimental Legislation: An Innovative Approach Towards Legalization *Thiago Hermont, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais; Fabiana de Menezes Soares, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais; Marcus Vinicius de Freitas Teixeira Leite, Universidade Federal de Minas Gerais*

In recent years, the regulation of the use and cultivation of cannabis has been discussed worldwide, especially motivated by initiatives from different countries to legalize both recreational and medical use. After the legalization in 2018, the Canadian government made available various informative materials on matters related to the regulation, informing society about the possible risks and the potential benefits of consumption. The controversial aspect surrounding the debate on the use of cannabis highlights a typical case for experimental legislation, in which the normative drafting process seeks to alleviate uncertainties and evaluate the advantages that might be achieved with the actual regulation of the matter. The experimentation considers time and space limitations, focusing on a restricted target audience, and evaluating the steps of implementation, monitoring and analysis of the results obtained. Some of the potential benefits of an experimental regulation are related to the production of tested knowledge to assess the norms being studied, which not only avoids errors in diagnosis and perception, but also overcomes information asymmetries between legislators and those impacted by the regulation. The regulatory impact assessment carried out in Brazil, as well as the Canadian governmental design of legislative drafting, demonstrate the need to revisit and discuss the context of experimental legislation when evaluating the advantages and obstacles of the legalization of cannabis.

Legitimation Of Expertise In Online Health Communities - Controversies in A French Speaking Forum *Stéphane Djahanchahi, Université de Bourgogne Franche-Comté; Benoit Cordelier, Université du Québec à Montréal*

(UQAM); *Olivier Galibert, Université de Bourgogne Franche-Comté (France)*

Our post-industrial societies are defined by a revolution in our relationship with knowledge, increased by the generalization of communications linked to the multiplication of ICT. Information from various sources is coming into opposition on different subjects, especially healthcare. Defiance of State authority is becoming widespread as health scandals grow. Official expertise no longer enjoys consensus and is in competition with others more secular forms acknowledged by a growing part of the public as mistrust of public institutions increases. This is all the most exemplary in the study of cannabis therapeutic applications. Nowadays, this is a very dynamic field of medical research, particularly in the fight against cancer, in terms of supportive care but also for the antitumor activity of certain cannabinoids such as THC and CBD. It is nonetheless still very controversial. It hence leads to the legitimization of alternative modes of knowledge production even in opposition to the legal framework, the media moral normativity. In this communication, we draw from an online ethnography and a discursive analysis of French language cannabis forums exploring and debating the production and use of therapeutic cannabis. We analyze the legitimization of expertise in online health communities by questioning their relationship with the medical authorities (1). We offer a taxonomy based on three modes of legitimization we identify as being decisive in qualifying the experts in these spaces (2). Finally, we propose a model for validating the expertise of the members of these online communities (3).

The applicability and effectiveness of “habeas corpus” in relation to the therapeutic use of cannabis in Brazil *Marcello Dantas Brandão, UECE - Universidade Estadual do Ceará; MARCELO RIBEIRO UCHÔA, UNIFOR*

Brazil does not currently have a legislation aimed to regulate the uses of cannabis and its derivatives. However, in some human health treatments refractory to other therapeutic strategies, cannabis derivatives have been employed to good effect. Thus, in December 2019, Anvisa (National Health Surveillance Agency) approved the RDC 327/2019, that finally indicated clearer guidelines on the issue. A part of the disputes over the right to treat conditions with this drug has reached the judicial sphere and we are investigating judicial processes on the matter with the double purpose of understand how pain has been highlighted in the decision making process, but also how the legal instrument of “habeas corpus” has gained applicability and effectiveness for people interested in treating their pains in a country where conservative values have been on the rise. This leads one to believe that the proposed changes in legislation, regarding cannabis, will be turned down by the National Congress, because the matter is associated with the behavioral agenda that is currently stuck in the Brazilian parliament. As such, the Executive, through a set of administrative tools (such as the above mentioned RDC of ANVISA) and the Judicial branches have been urged to find alternatives to enable the usage of cannabis that is able to provide verifiable positive impacts on living standards. In this paper, we focus on the applicability and the effectiveness of the legal instrument of “habeas corpus”, through a comparative analysis of a corpus composed of 43 decisions in favor and a dozen decisions against the therapeutic use of cannabis and its derivatives.

Session Organizers:

Daniela Leandro Rezende, Universidade Federal de Ouro Preto
Paulo Fraga, Universidade Federal de Juiz de Fora

Chair:

Victor Luiz Alves Mourao, Federal University of Viçosa (UFV-Brazil)

Discussant:

João Tabora da Gama, Universidade Católica Portuguesa

064. Centering Public Healthcare III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Though healthcare provides fundamental conditions of (im)possibility for life in the places we research, the workings of public (socialized, employment-based, welfare state) healthcare often remain both allusive and elusive in the studies of science, technology, and medicine (STM). While conceiving of healthcare provision, access, and policy as underlying analyses of biomedical knowledge production, patient-doctor relationships, and illness subjectivities, we seldom explore in depth the co-constitutive forces of the knowledges, practices, and technologies involved in producing, operating, maintaining, and transforming public healthcare. Healthcare structures index particular histories, ethics, and ideologies. They represent a foundational politics of life baked into institutions, pre-structuring care relationships, and organizing social life and membership. They can be a source of stability, solidarity, and social prosperity, much as they generate gaps and uncertainties, strategic ignorances and bureaucracies of exclusion. We invite fellow STM scholars to help us develop better vocabulary, methods, and theories for understanding and analyzing practices of administering and the administration of public healthcare.

Participants:

(In)effective And (Un)friendly Communication In Public Healthcare In Russia: Navigating Institutional Inconsistencies *Anastasiia Andreevna Novkunskaia, European University at St. Petersburg*

Over the past decades, the healthcare system in Russia has undergone multiple changes, affecting both its institutional arrangement and the practice of interpersonal interaction. The commercialization of medicine, the consumerization of patient behavior, the emergence of new medical approaches (Temkina 2016, 2017), changes in professional standards of care and other processes have set complex settings in which social norms and expectations turn out to be multiple, contradictory and changeable. Despite the volatility of this context, some forms of communication between key participants of multiple interactions in it remain stable and have been reproduced since the Soviet period. In particular, the “Soviet approach” was recognized as paternalistic (Rivkin-Fish 2005), that is, assuming an asymmetry of power between patients and medical professionals, between the latter and the management of clinics, as well as between the system of healthcare and the state ideology (Saks 2015). Despite all the reforms carried out since the early 1990s, the context of healthcare institutions in Russia remains largely “unfriendly” to patients and reproduces inequality both at the level of social structures and at the level of everyday communications between key actors. This project, basing on qualitative semi-structured interviews with health practitioners and patients, addresses the sustainability of the rude and unfriendly forms of communication (for at least one of its parties). In addition, the study aims to analyze, in what forms actually undesirable communication between patients and medical practitioners, or between representatives of different professional groups, can be carried out in Russian healthcare currently.

Medical disposals and problem solving. About high blood pressure (Morocco) *Josiane Carine Tantchou, Cnrs*

I analyze how in basic health-care facilities in Morocco, general practitioners transform patients’ problems into solvable problems, taking into account constraints related to medical standards, financial issues, the organization of the health system, and care. My focus is on hypertension, or high blood pressure. I argue that standards allow the solving of patients’ problems through the production of an entity called high blood pressure. However, the ‘high blood pressure’ enacted is different from the entity defined by standards. Fragments of the latter, borrowed from other contexts, are put to work in Morocco, while the material arrangements needed to enforce and have them work without discontinuities do not exist. This contributes to the

production of an entity configured at a moment in time between standards and patients' lives.

Reflexivity in moral decision-making: assessing and managing child abuse and domestic violence *Jetske Erisman, Athena Institute, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Barbara Regeer*

Many countries are reporting increases in domestic violence and child abuse rates and intensity during the Covid-19 pandemic. This pervasive, complex, and sensitive issue requires careful responses from child welfare organisations. Signs of abuse – often hidden and open to interpretation – can be difficult to detect and assess, and processes rely on the personal judgement of social workers and professionals. Acknowledgement of the complexities of abuse has led to attempts at reorganising the field and reducing uncertainties of practice through the provision of standardised assessments, guidelines and instruments, a trend also observed in the Netherlands. Concurrently, there is a recognition of the importance of professionals' personal judgement and the need for reflexive practice and use of different knowledges, such as intuition. There is an opportunity for guidelines to support reflection and intuition as part of 'good care' practice, but we have found that on the ground, professionals fear malpractice accusations. By conducting in-depth interviews with professionals and observations of their multi-disciplinary discussions, this paper explores how good reflexivity can be achieved in highly charged moral settings at the intersection of the multiple marginalizations of domestic violence and child abuse. We particularly focus on how professionals navigate complexities, and what the role is of regulatory infrastructures, including guidelines and protocols in framing their interaction with the child welfare system.

Securing health care within a 'magical' state: the construction of eligibility for low-income treatment schemes in urban India *Lesley Branagan*

In India, marginalised people with serious or chronic illness face particular challenges to finding sustainable treatment, and often experience financial devastation. One state welfare scheme (the EWS hospital bed quotas) holds the promise of treatment for those in Delhi's margins, through partnerships with corporate hospitals. Yet, the process of gaining access to the scheme is very frustrating. This ethnography illustrates the ways in which low-income patients' attempts to lay claim to state services often bring them into play with a mode of the state that is, in anthropologists' conceptions, opaque, arbitrary, erratic, "magical" and illegible. In response to the illegible modes of access to the scheme, patients and their families are compelled to construct and reproduce their eligibility to access treatment through a repertoire of intricate and entwined practices, namely: the attainment of credible low-income documentation, the use of big men to leverage resources, and different kinds of performance. The burden of enacting these practices is exacerbated for patients who need ongoing access to treatment that is dependent on technology, such as dialysis. It is further compounded and troubled by the state scheme's blurry entanglement with the private sector, in which roles and responsibilities for a 'duty of care' to citizens with illness are elusive. This paper therefore aims to be an original contribution to the social sciences and STS, in interpreting health-seekers' experiences of state-private schemes in Delhi that promise to provide access to technology, within anthropological understandings of the state and marginalised people's meaning-making of illegible state processes.

Session Organizers:

Shoshana Deuth, Cornell University

Lisa Lehner, Cornell University

065. Citizen Science as Method - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Participants:

Participant perspectives on citizen science knowledge

production *Sofie Verkest, Ghent University; Huib Huyse, KU Leuven*

Citizen science (CS) has been heralded for its democratising, educational and scientific potential (Bonney et al., 2014; Ottinger, 2016). We follow Strasser et al. (2019, p. 65) in their claim that CS deserves discursive scrutiny, and set out to explore its "potential for transforming who can produce legitimate knowledge and what we know about the world" by turning to one key group of stakeholders that has been understudied so far, viz. citizen participants themselves. Research on CS tends to focus on its outcomes (e.g. public understanding of science) rather than on the lived experiences of participants. In this paper, we combine large scale surveys with focus groups with participants of one CS project during and after the project to examine participants' experiences, and how their participation affects their views on the scientific process and products. More specifically, we aim to find out how participants construct epistemologies of CS and the outcomes of CS as (counter-)expertise or as (il)legitimate. We focus on the participants of "CurieuzNeuzen in de tuin", a large-scale CS project measuring heat and humidity in Flemish gardens. This critical case study is especially relevant as it builds its science communication strategies on the experiences with the CurieuzNeuzen Vlaanderen project, considered best practice in citizen science by the European Commission. Our study is embedded in a larger linguistic ethnographic study on collaboration and participation in science, one that has so far pointed out that, in spite of the ambitions of CS, little attention is paid to the citizens (Verkest & Jacobs, forthcoming).

Technologies for citizens: the role of documents *Morgan Meyer*

How are technologies and scientific equipment documented? Based on a study of low-tech and do-it-yourself biology, this paper shows that documentation must be conceived as a method in itself, as it mobilizes different practices and various formats: tutorials that present "cookbook recipes" for technologies, reports that assess experimentations in a scientific way, and videos that stage technologies as key actors in ecological lifestyles. The paper shows that documents not only record how technologies can be experimented with and how alternative scientific equipment can be built. The documents analyzed in this paper combine two different genres: technical and factual descriptions and, on the other hand, poetic and aesthetic narration, with personalized accounts, humor, and dramatization. The combination of these genres positions technologies for citizens as both doable and desirable. Documentation is not thus only concerned with the description and making of material technologies, it also reveals and performs the wider significances, values and pleasures of the act of making.

Tracing Hyperlinks: How to support different forms of presence and knowledge production in an online citizen science community? *Björn Ekström, University of Borås; Corey Jackson, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Carsten Østerlund, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University*

Over the past decade there have been significant improvements in the organizational infrastructures supporting information sharing, retrieval, storage, and use. At present, users with access to online applications can post, read, evaluate, vote for, and elaborate on information sources of all shapes and stripes. In citizen science, this is manifested in projects focusing on volunteer classification of readily available data. While such projects adopt standardized methods for data classification, virtual discussion boards provide possibilities for peers to confer about method uncertainties. In such environments, it is important to explore how emerging organizational forms and sociomaterial dynamics shape a range of knowledge production opportunities. Some might be facilitated by experts providing tutorials which

resemble classroom teaching while others emerge out of collective work on discussion boards or agent-centered explorations where participants build hyperlinked resource libraries. Through practices of hyperlinking, digital sources of internal and external information can be drawn into the discussion boards to facilitate debates and conversations, mitigating classification uncertainties. Problematizing standardized methods in relation to peer knowledge from discussion boards, we compare volunteers' knowledge production practices in a citizen science project on Zooniverse.org. Taking our point of departure in practice theory (Gherardi 2019; Østerlund, Crowston, Jackson 2020), we combine insights from studies of collaborative knowledge production with a sociomaterial informed theory of learning articulated by the STS scholar Sørensen (2009). This is done to unfold how hyperlinking practices expand standardized data classification methods and performatively shape knowledge production in a citizen science project.

Session Organizer:

Yasuhito Abe, Komazawa University

066. New Wars on Science III - Lay Knowledge and Mobilizations

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Participants:

Life in a (re)mystified world: conspiracy, digital knowledge, and the (re)shaping of the world. *Harry Dyer*, University of East Anglia

The internet has facilitated the resurgence of a number of extreme fringe beliefs, providing spaces for like-minded people to discuss their ideas. One growing fringe group has received little academic exploration, despite picking up a wealth of media attention and a number of noted celebrity followers. That is the resurrection of a belief in a 'flat earth'. Exploring their presence may help us understand numerous issues, such as the current scepticism towards science, the rise of disinformation, and the manner in which social media is (re)shaping the ways we experience, known, navigate, and live in a world whose very structure is a point of contention. Reporting on ethnographic field notes taken from a 3-day UK flat earth convention, this paper discusses what this phenomenon tells us about knowledge in a post-truth world. The findings highlight a case to re-examine some of the early 20th century conceptualisations of modernity. In particular, Foucault's claims about the intimate relationship between power and knowledge, for example, face new challenges when communities such as Flat Earthers attempt to decouple claims to knowledge from traditional institutions of research bound up in knowledge and power. Similarly, Weber's arguments around the increasingly scientific nature of modernity come into question when communities for a range of reasons are remystifying the world around them in a way that is reminiscent of Baudrillard's ideas of a media-infused hyper-reality. In a post truth world, the shaping of reality itself is seemingly up for grabs, and new knowledges are being constructed.

Public Perceptions of Science, Scientists and Scientific Controversies: A Qualitative Study Exploring How US Americans Discuss Their Trust in Science *Emily Blosser*, The University of Louisiana at Lafayette; *Carson carson.strang1@louisiana.edu* *Strang*, University of Louisiana Lafayette

Public trust in science is an important issue in the United States that has not been widely explored using qualitative research methods. Quantitative research finds that a majority of US Americans believe that science positively influences society. However, it is well documented that there is an increasing level of political polarization with respect to certain scientific controversies. It is also well established that trust in scientific

experts has declined significantly among political conservatives. In this paper, using in-depth interviews conducted in one southern state in the USA, we present preliminary findings on this topic. We describe how respondents discuss their perceptions of various scientific controversies, the role they want scientists to play in public life, and how they make decisions about which scientific facts and scientists to trust. This paper draws on perspectives from STS that recognize that social forces have a profound influence on scientific knowledge production and perceptions of science. We highlight the challenges and opportunities that scientists, activists, and politicians face in convincing the public about what constitutes legitimate and trustworthy science, as well as how political identity influences perceptions of science, scientists and scientific controversies.

The Science of the Manosphere *Julia DeCook*, Loyola University Chicago

After years of violent attacks, incels and the larger "Manosphere" have cemented their place in the public lexicon and imagination, often depicted as a group of angry (young, white) men who are bonded together by their spectacular misogyny. Despite intense media, scholarly, and practitioner scrutiny of incels and other male supremacist movements, little discussion has been had about the ways that these groups use archives and other modes of knowledge production to legitimize their beliefs. Drawing from a 3-year online ethnography of these groups, this presentation examines the ways that male supremacists engage in knowledge production via their establishment of wikis, archives, and research articles drafted by members. Although misogyny is their main organizing principle, incels are drawn together by a larger project to convince "normies" of the "scientific" basis of the "sexual marketplace" and inceldom, which is often steeped in eugenics, and scientific justifications for their misogynistic beliefs. Using the lens of Clarke and Star's theory of social worlds as well as Stoler's conception of archives representing social epistemologies, this presentation examines the ways that incels and other Manosphere groups attempt to engage in truth-making processes, attempting to challenge "mainstream" science and culture, via the affordances of digital infrastructure.

Session Organizers:

Henri Boullier, French National Centre for Scientific Research (CNRS)

Baptiste Kotras, INRAE, LISIS

067. Digital Inclusion In Practices - I: Digital inclusion in public action

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Constructing the Digital Skills Crisis: A Critical Conceptual History of "Skill" *Lauren E Bridges*, Annenberg School of Communication, University of Pennsylvania; *Zane Griffin Talley Cooper*, University of Pennsylvania, Annenberg School for Communication; *Julia Ticona Ticona*, University of Pennsylvania, Annenberg School for Communication

There is a digital skills crisis: the digital skills crisis does not exist. Through a conceptual history of skill—a word, concept, and action—this paper analyzes the historical, cultural, and material constructions of skill and how it has come to influence current discourse around the alleged "digital skills crisis". Rather than an intrinsic quality to be acquired, we show how skill has been deployed as a political concept to order bodies and processes according to the interests of power and capital. Pushing back against skilled/unskilled dichotomies, we argue skill itself has been used as a technology in the division of labor (Marx, 1990) to maintain patriarchal (Berg, 1994), and colonial hierarchies (Kumar, 2018). This genealogy helps situate how skill is conceptually operationalized alongside technology in

contemporary politics. Through a systematic analysis of policy and public speech from four US presidents—from Clinton’s push to bridge the “digital divide” to Trump’s executive order to “combat the skills crisis”—we show how skills discourse is framed as a deficit issue in service of political ends. By centering the conceptual roots of skill, this paper attempts to reclaim an understanding of skills as collective social knowledge that are essential to, and not separate from, technology (Veblen, 1914). Through this work, we hope to generate a broader discussion about the normative assumptions which tie the idea of skill to technological progress so we may reimagine the kinds of collective social knowledge we need to produce a more just and equitable future.

(Digital) Welfare for All? Disabled People and their Relatives as Participants and Non-Users in Denmark’s Digital State
Barbara Nino Carreras, IT University of Copenhagen

Statistics seem to confirm that Denmark’s digital welfare is a success because most citizens use public digital self-services. Yet, a new disability rights movement called #enmillionstemmer (#onemillionvotes) seems to disrupt such reality. Despite inclusion initiatives performed by the Agency for Digitization, disabled people and their relatives’ rights do not seem to be sufficiently covered. The movement, initiated in 2019, indicates that welfare provision for disabled people and their relatives is insufficient and oppressive. In recent years, scholars have unfolded patterns of exclusion in the mandatory digitalization of welfare services. The participation of disabled people and their relatives in protecting their rights in recent digital reforms of the public sector is widely under-examined. This paper takes on an ethnographic approach and draws from Adele Clarke’s situational analysis to explore a mix of archival materials and interviews that compare #onemillionvotes’ motivations, and inclusion initiatives performed by the Agency for Digitization. The paper questions whether the public sector’s mandatory digitalization excludes disabled people and their relatives in participating in what constitutes equal and sufficient (digital) welfare. Building on literature from disability studies, participatory design, and feminist STS, the paper critically maps out user research and the agency’s participatory methods. The paper problematizes user research and inclusion strategies that understand disabled people as non-digital citizens. Finally, the paper speculates on participatory methods, where disabled people and their relatives lead and participate in how they are supported as users of public services, that are not always digital.

Imagining, Representing and Including Minority Populations in Noncommercial Data Based Projects
Lucie Delias, Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM)

Generalization of Big Data, and the resulting “datafication” of society (Mayer-Schönberger & Cukier, 2013) complexifies the notion of digital inequalities—and its associated forms of exclusions (Robinson et al., 2020; Carmi & Yates, 2020). In this framework, this paper investigates how the professionals involved in non-commercial data-driven projects envision the inclusion and participation of citizens who are not familiar with digital tools, especially those from minorities (Laplanche-Servigne & Sa Vilas Boas, 2019). Based on the collective research project “The Datafication of Society: Sociopolitical issues in the production and use of public and private data” (UQAM), my paper will look closer at two projects: Montreal City’s open data portal and a Quebec health data sharing public platform. I will investigate those from a Critical Data Studies and STS theoretical perspective, plus a qualitative methodology based on the analysis of institutional documentation and interviews with the professionals involved in those projects. The aim of this research is to explore tensions between the official discourse, sometimes tainted by technophilia—representing data as a means to create social change benefiting everyone—and the concrete actions and tools implemented to encourage the participation of people belonging to minority populations.

Session Organizer:

Céline Borelle, SENSE - Orange labs / CEMS - CNRS

Chair:

Céline Borelle, SENSE - Orange labs / CEMS - CNRS

Discussant:

Valérie Peugeot, SENSE - Orange labs

068. Domesticating Pandemic Troubles: Modelling Covid-19 in an Uncertain World III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Modelling, a scientific practice once reserved for mathematicians, epidemiologists, ecologists and economists, has assumed sudden authority in the covid-19 pandemic. The commanding presence of models in global policy has prompted questions about evidence, reliability and trust. Predictions and forecasting, grounded in formalised assumptions, have shifted the landscape of acceptable evidence in global public health. Moreover, modelling became popular: scores of armchair epidemiologists shared their newfound wisdom, the R-number and “exponential growth” became household terminology, while hashtags like #flattenthecurve entangled “science into social practices, calculations into materialisations, abstracts into affects.” (Rhodes et al 2020) In this panel, we will survey how pandemic modelling made relations since early 2020. We will reflect on the unprecedented ways in which pandemic modelling engaged with unequal and uncertain worlds. We encourage two kinds of contributions: 1) papers which consider the impact of pandemic modelling on knowledge production, policymaking and social relations in pandemic times. Such papers might ask what models do and how they perform as evidence and how modelling has shifted, accelerated or reconfigured persisting challenges of inequality, racism and colonialism. Authors might pay attention to local, regional or national frames of reference. 2) Papers, which investigate the making of relations within models and scrutinize how practices of modelling enfold social, geographical, ecological and microbiological assumptions when forecasting the pandemic world. We invite papers focusing particularly beyond Europe and North America to ask what constitutes good relations within modelling practices, and how we might reconcile these with an ethics of care, responsibility and solidarity.

Participants:

‘Evidence-Enough’ in Uncertain Worlds: The Ontological Politics of Enacting Mathematical Models as Evidence
Kari Lancaster, University of New South Wales, Sydney; Tim Rhodes, Centre for Social Research in Health, UNSW

Mathematical models are playing a critical role in policy decision-making and public communications, as a means of taming the uncertainties of the present and intervening in the face of the unknown. What constitutes ‘evidence’ – and more specifically ‘evidence-enough’ – for intervention and response is being revised in science and policy, shaped by the urgency of evolving situations. Covid-19 throws into sharp relief the need for more nuanced thinking about the nature of the thing we call ‘evidence’, beyond that offered in ‘evidence-based policy’ accounts. Drawing on insights from science and technology studies, this paper invites a shift away from thinking with evidence primarily as a matter of epistemology and instead takes evidence as an ontological concern, illuminating how the thing we call ‘evidence’ is enacted in practices. We take the case of mathematical models in contemporary epidemic responses, noticing how they perform and travel as ‘evidence’. We focus on how boundaries are made around what constitutes ‘evidence-enough’ for intervention and response, especially through controversies, resistance and challenge, delimiting what models can and cannot do. Urgent and evolving situations of need remind us that there are always degrees of uncertainty and that outcomes are without guarantee. An approach that attends to the multiple enactments of ‘evidence’ is not only relevant in crisis periods, however. It is a lens which allows us to notice the legitimising and authorising practices at work and the coordinating relational linkages between them, with implications

for evidence-making and intervening in the everyday.

Pandemic Times: Mathematical Models and the Coordination of COVID Futures *Catherine Montgomery, University of Edinburgh; Steve Sturdy; Lukas Engelmann, University of Edinburgh*

In this paper we examine the role of the UK print media in constructing pandemic time through reports on government policy and its relationship with pandemic modelling. The latter has been a prominent feature of public and political discourse in relation to COVID-19, with folk epidemiology entering the mainstream on social media through the hashtag #flattenthecurve and politicians publicly avowing they were 'following the science'. The science here refers to pandemic models produced by UK-based academics and made available to the Scientific Advisory Group on Emergencies (SAGE), responsible for advising the government on its response to COVID-19. Outbreak modelling has variously been analysed as metaphor, a symbolic vehicle for gaining authority, socio-epistemic 'glue', and, more recently, a form of anticipatory governance. Here, we draw on Tavory & Eliasoph's (2013) theoretical work on modes of future-making to analyse the entwined work of media and models in the coordination of COVID futures. During times of crisis and social upheaval – what Tavory and Eliasoph refer to as "eventful situations" – people have to piece together a new temporal landscape, in which an evolving order (social, political, economic) creates the possibility for new trajectories, and a recalibration of the everyday. Here, we analyse the production of temporal possibilities in the UK media and modelling's role in delimiting these.

Prediction Abandoned: Japanese cases of COVID-19 and nuclear disaster *Shin-etsu SUGAWARA, Kansai University; Kohta Juraku, Tokyo Denki University*

As risks become more complex and systemic, risk governance studies have put more focus on symbolic anticipation of danger with taking full advantage of computer simulation in place of the conventional trial-and-error approach. When looking closely at the process of predictive simulation, contrary to its alleged neutrality and monolithic claims of scientific certainty, it inevitably entails human judgment when setting purposes, approximating realities, defining metrics, and providing implications for informed decision making. Reflecting the rich insight from the STS literature elucidating the process how we know what we know, it is such plurality and conditionality of predictions that can ramify and contextualize future images and thus can be a key to cope better with uncertain future. Recent Japanese cases of COVID-19 and nuclear technological disaster show, however, predictive simulations were firstly mobilized as the unique scientific evidence of governmental policies, but soon became contested socially and politically, and eventually vanished from policy making arena. The opening up of knowledge generation process seems to serve not to shed light on the plurality and conditionality of predictions for public scrutiny and for scientifically and socially justified policy decisions, but to highlight the arbitrariness of human judgment and to eliminate it. The authors will explore the background of these phenomena reflecting the concept of "grass-roots" technological hubris which they presented last year, and how the STS scholarship would address it.

Session Organizer:

Steve Sturdy

069. Food for care: Interrogating practices of eating in troubled worlds - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

How care manifests (or not) in everyday encounters with food and practices of eating in? How to nourish relations of care while nourishing the bodies? Studies from STS, food anthropology, and sociology present a variety of

accounts of food-induced socialites and socio-material relations (production challenges, security and environmental change, boundaries between the eater and the eaten, digitalisation and platformization of food, etc). This panel attends to the mundane and everyday instances of relating to, with and through eating. Mundane encounters with food manifest social class, gendered work division, colonial attitudes, socio-economic inequalities, and the moral balance between health and pleasure. Responsibilization of eating and cooking transforms the kitchen and the dining table into a boundary terrain for public health campaigns, environmental concerns, and hedonistic searches for pleasure. This panel asks what is or can be neglected as we care for what and how we eat? Especially as sanitary regimes of lockdowns, confinements, and curfews forefront eating in and intensify invisible work. We invite multidisciplinary works which tackle eating as a learned, trained, proceduralized, and performed practice shaping relations to science, governance, health, pleasure, solidarity, and care. We welcome attention to the embodied aspect of eating and cooking, including interactions with products, elements, instruments, and technology. Following food studies scholars, submissions may be analytically focused on three points and their interrelations: social occasions, food selections, and processes of body incorporation. Finally, we are curious about methodological and speculative reflections on the transformative side of research into the practices of eating. This session the first session of the panel subtitled "Food systems on the move: Regimes, values, and (non)care practices in more-than-human worlds"

Participants:

The management of food work in the French regime of reproduction: reforms and social inequalities *Sebastian Pizarro Erazo, LISE - Laboratoire Interdisciplinaire pour la Sociologie Économique*

This proposal adopts as its object the regime of reproduction in contemporary French society, that is, a social system of practices for taking charge of the production and reproduction activities of individuals. Food activities then integrate a large and diversified set of activities participating in the recomposition of human energies. This regime is characterized by the implementation of several reforms encouraging families to delegate domestic activities to other social actors, including the market and the extended family. In this way, the public authorities intend to support families in the production of day-to-day well-being and to promote their ability to meet commitments in different spheres of social life (professional, civic, leisure, etc.). Based on fieldwork consisting of interviews and observations conducted in the Ile-de-France region with 38 families from different social backgrounds, this proposal aims to analyze the effects of these reforms on the practices of taking charge of food activities among families. We start from the hypothesis that in the French socio-institutional framework, reproductive activities are part of social relations structured on the basis of gender, social background and cultural origin, which participate, moreover, in the reproduction of social inequalities. We will analyze the practices of taking charge of the activities from the angles of gender and socio-cultural origins. This proposal therefore seeks to show how the French regime of reproductive activities, including food work, encourages social inequalities between families in the participation in the professional, civic and learning spheres.

A Plate Full of Food and Care - Food Practices Between Sustainability, Practicality and Pleasure *Suse Brettn, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin; Sandra Čajić, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*

In current debates about a sustainable food system, the household is often addressed as a place of socio-ecological transformation. Likewise discussed are potentials and limits of existing and new ways of food provisioning - be it local, consumer-driven cooperatives or digital platforms. However, so far little is known about the influence of these different forms of food provisioning on the actual food practices in the household. The research

project PLATEFORMS addresses this gap by using qualitative-participatory methods for research in households in and around Berlin. In our paper we would like to present our results embedded in a perspective of care. We want to create a transformative approach by perceiving food related care practices as socially and ecologically intertwined and thus focusing both on individual values and practices as well as on structural conditions for sustainability. Results of our research show that the participants want to act ethically and politically 'correct' and socio-ecological concerns can be seen as one of their principles. From a feminist point of view, however, a critical look at the compatibility of care and sustainability is necessary: Quite often participants experience a strong tension between their ethical-political principals, the everyday life and the realities of the food system. Nonetheless, our findings show that some forms of food provisioning are better suited to go around this discrepancy than others and that household practices are often driven by practices of mindfulness and relatedness (Conradi, 2001).

Beyond the Dietary Shift: Slow Food Activism and Its Care-ful Composition of Values *Anneke Boersma, Athena Institute, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Evelien de Hoop, Athena Institute, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Teun Zuiderent-Jerak, Athena Institute, VU Amsterdam*

With biodiversity loss, a climate crisis, hunger and increased numbers of patients with food-related non-communicable diseases, change of our food system is crucial. It has led to widespread calls for a 'dietary shift' in which 80% of our global protein intake has to be plant-based. The Slow Food movement shares these socio-ecological concerns, but the call for a dietary shift is largely absent from its discourse and practices. Slow Food activists rather emphasize the practices within the food chain that are care-ful and their focus on food that is 'good, clean and fair' requires the avoidance of just one target. This paper draws upon engaged fieldwork among slow food activists taking part in an online challenge to learn about and enact slow food practices. Social media posts, online conversations and calls with participants and ambassadors brought to the fore that a dietary shift is incidental to a passion for food and the desire to partake in the food chain. The latter ambitions are driven by multiple values, and require keeping those values together rather than singling out a value (or a few) to create a stand-alone target (Heuts & Mol, 2013). Indeed, successful realization of Slow Food's comprehensive ambitions based on a care-ful composition of values requires the active exclusion of the dominance of some values (Zuiderent-Jerak, Grit & van der Grinten, 2015), such as a pre-set percentage of plant-based protein intake. Heuts, F., & Mol, A. (2013). What Is a Good Tomato? A Case of Valuing in Practice. *Valuation Studies*, 1(2), 125-146. doi:10.3384/vs.2001-5992.1312125 Zuiderent-Jerak, T., Grit, K., & Grinten van der, T. (2015) Critical composition of public values: On the enactment and disarticulation of what counts in health-care markets. In I. Dussauge, C. F. Helgesson & F. Lee (Eds.), *Value Practices in the Life Sciences and Medicine* (pp. 119 - 135). Oxford, UK: Oxford University Press

Caring for Meat? Navigating Contradictory Relations in Mundane Eating Practices *Outi Koskinen, University of Helsinki*

In recent years, calls to care for the various harmful dimensions of meat eating have proliferated. These include detrimental environmental impacts of meat production, adverse health effects of ingesting red and processed meats, as well as the thorny ethical issues related to killing animals. However, alongside these relations that would encourage disentangling ourselves from meat eating, there are also various caring relations within meat eating. For example, through meat it is possible to pamper loved ones, entertain guests, or look after one's vitality through self-care. In this presentation, I ask how consumers navigate these contradictory relations of care inherent in meat eating.

Based on interview and participant observation data of consumers with a wide range of meat eating practices in Finland, I discuss the complex care relations that (dis)connect humans, other animals, and the ethical/political within mundane practices of eating meat. The presentation therefore connects to STS discussions that see caring as more-than-human relations that, crucially, are inevitably bounded and partial – it is impossible to relate caringly to everything at once. The main argument of the presentation is within the studied practices of mundane meat eating, contradictory care relations are navigated through moderating care. This refers to the distances and disconnections, hesitations and realignments that can diminish care while not leading to total disengagement from it. Therefore, moderation highlights how, somewhat paradoxically, partial caring relations can at the same time sensitize us to some of the harmful consequences of food practices, while still not automatically leading to changing them.

Preventive Health Tests Practices, Food, and Eating: How to Care in Fairer Ways for Bodies in Biomedicalized Food Cultures? *Myriam Durocher*

In contemporary biomedicalized food cultures (Durocher, 2020), care is partly enacted through practices aimed at testing one's body to evaluate and prevent potential health risks associated with the diet. Several medical and chronic conditions such as obesity and diabetes are thought in relation to diet. In an era marked with the fear of fatness, chronic diseases, and other conditions associated with eating, prevention and condition management testing practices become means to care for bodies, in the present as much as in the future. The interpretation of these testing/monitoring practices and their results lead to the proposition of dietary advice in order to prevent or fix any seemingly diet-related health problems. Many critical food and fat studies scholars have argued that prevention practices and discourses, and public health measures aiming to "solve" the obesity "epidemic" are loaded with fat phobia and work towards the discrimination of fat bodies (Counihan & Van Esterik, 2008; Gard & Wright, 2005; Guthman, 2013; Monaghan et al., 2013; Rich & Evans, 2005; Saguy, 2014). Critical food studies scholars have also pointed out how this way of enacting care through food and eating is reductive of the complexity of the relationships between food and health (Overend, 2020; Sanabria & Yates-Doerr, 2015; Scrinis, 2013) and neglects a whole range of other factors that inform health, however the latter is defined (Gálvez et al., 2020). Additionally, these scholars have highlighted how such a medicalized way of approaching food ignores many other dimensions (affective, relational, emotional, environmental) of food and eating. This presentation asks: what is neglected when we care for bodies through testing their materialities and orienting their diet with the hope of preventing health related conditions? Could we envision different ways, more socially and environmentally just, to care for (human and more than human) bodies? Drawing on critical food studies literature that mobilizes research in environmental epigenetics as well as on feminist posthumanist researchers investigating the porosity of bodies, I discuss how current ways of caring for human bodies with relation to food and eating neglects a whole range of social and environmental injustices that materialize in one's body and health.

Salty encounters: How to study 'good relations' with salt? *Alexandra Endaltseva, CNRS - CERTOP; Anne Dupuy Hoang, Université de Toulouse Jean Jaurès/ CERTOP UMR-CNRS 5044*

Salt (sodium chloride) is a chemical compound embedded solidly in cooking and eating routines and practices. It is a precious companion to conservation, recipes, table decoration, and gustative appreciations. However, salt overconsumption (Brown et al, 2009; Eyles et al, 2016) is one of the top two dietary risk factors contributing majorly to cardiovascular-related deaths. The

current mean of salt intake is almost twice the recommended by the WHO (in the member countries) and the figures are predicted to increase. Relations with salts, good or bad, form as multiple knowledges (scientific, policy, experiential, practical, embodied) get translated into salting practices (Poulain, 2002). This translation process between the lay and scientific knowledges, aesthetic values and public health concerns requires care for how to analyze everyday salting practices from a relational and ecosystemic perspective, taking seriously material interactions of salt itself (with/within different products, for example). We ground this paper in ethnographic and experimental work within the French project "Sal&Mieux: Optimizing the use of discretionary salt" which aims to better understand and, consequentially to 'improve' discretionary salt intake. We trace how the ethnography of practices travels into experimental protocols, instantiating our puzzles of studying 'good' and 'bad' relations with salt. With a feminist STS commitment to thinking with care, we wonder how to account for embodiment work (Endaltseva and Jerak-Zuiderent, 2021), aesthetic values (Pols, 2019), relations with food pleasure (Dupuy & Poulain, 2012; Dupuy, 2013), taste freedom and collective orders of sensing (Voß and Guggenheim, 2019) when shaping scientifically knowledge of 'good' salting.

Session Organizer:

Anne Dupuy Hoang, Université de Toulouse Jean Jaurès/
CERTOP UMR-CNRS 5044

Chair:

Alexandra Endaltseva, CNRS - CERTOP

070. Disciplinary Translations in Science and Society - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Recent events worldwide have shown the relevance of interdisciplinary approaches to cope with uncertainty: the current pandemic and sanitary crisis, social and political protests, climate emergency -among many others- prove the need to think—and act—in novel and creative ways. More than disciplines examining phenomena from different standpoints, innovative interdisciplinary approaches need to conceptualize past and emerging problems from assemblages at the interaction of various fields. In this way, effective interdisciplinary studies could contribute to understanding our world from a more complex, dense, and purposeful perspective. At the crossroads of society and science, STS offers a strong potential to trespass traditional knowledge production boundaries. This panel seeks to explore the role of "disciplinary translations" in studying science and societies. Disciplinary translations refer to the transfer of concepts, ideas, frameworks produced in science and applied to understand social dilemmas and vice versa. To mention just a few examples, there have been experiences of applying complex models of physics to understand social networks; chaos theory to study social behaviors in crowds; chemical transformations in matter to analyze historical processes. This panel aims to bring together proposals from different fields exploring this post-disciplinary approach to both science and society. Additionally, the purpose of this panel is to discuss how STS could contribute to shaping both compelling and effective interdisciplinary knowledge production.

Participants:

Access To Justice Design Lab: Bringing Solutions To Justice And Breaking Barriers Through Transdisciplinarity *Santiago de Francisco Vela*, Laboratorio de Diseño para la Justicia - Universidad de los Andes; *Laura Guzmán Abello*, Laboratorio de Diseño para la Justicia - Universidad de los Andes; *Santiago Pardo Rodríguez*, Laboratorio de Diseño para la Justicia - Universidad de los Andes; *Laura Vanessa Vanegas Herrera*, Laboratorio de Diseño para la Justicia - Universidad de los Andes; *Nicolls Feghali Vargas*, Laboratorio de Diseño para la Justicia - Universidad de los Andes; *Camila Padilla Casas*, Laboratorio de Diseño para la Justicia - Universidad de los Andes

The law underlies roughly every aspect of people's lives, including health, employment, education, and entrepreneurship. In Colombia, the administration of justice has remained the same for decades, and millions of citizens have stopped trusting in the justice instances. On many occasions, this distrust responds to the various existent barriers, such as budgetary, language, geographic, cultural, and shortcomings in the service provided, covered by digital solutions. These barriers are more considerable for traditionally marginalized populations, especially after the Covid-19 pandemic. This paper shows the case of The Access to Justice Design Lab (A2JLab), which offers how socio-technical design approaches developed by transdisciplinary teams lead to successful cases and new challenges and opportunities in the resolution of digital transformation justice-related problems which are particularly complex. A2JLab involves a transdisciplinary educational, research, and consulting space led by engineers, designers, and lawyers. The main objective is to design and implement new solutions for justice through a shared conceptual framework that incorporates systems thinking, design thinking, and law rethinking. This case has been an example of transdisciplinarity in complex problems, which implies a significant challenge due to uncertainty. However, it opens new opportunities to rethink innovation in the legal and public spheres, putting the citizen and a purposeful perspective at the center and promoting access to justice, which enables and empowers people to tackle inequalities and barriers and participate in legal processes that promote inclusive growth.

Crime Narratives: a collaborative exploration in STS communication *Daniela Idrovo*, *Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*; *Maria Elissa Torres Carrasco*, *Kaleidos Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*

What do police reports and science fiction stories have in common? Building EthnoData—a multimedia platform on violent deaths and missing people in Ecuador—we learned that reality and science fiction are not as far apart as one might imagine. The team that designed the platform's architecture found that out of 6 471 violent deaths between 2014 and 2019 one in four intentional homicides was categorized as resulting from a "street fight". The category hides more than it reveals, so we closely analyzed over 3 000 cases. Beyond the violence, the detailed descriptions of these murders read more like fictional narratives than police reports. The circumstances of each death were described intertwining forensic, detective, and tabloid languages, triggering different kinds of imaginaries. EthnoData made use of these police-narrated violent stories for experimenting with different communication formats in a section called "Crime Narratives." The process included reading cases from the Police and Attorney General's databases, anonymizing them, and reviewing press releases—mainly tabloids and crime chronicles related to those deaths. The section aimed at contextualizing crime through different narratives, languages, and formats. In this paper, we offer a description of the making of "disciplinary translations," by which we mean the process that we undertook to turn crime narratives from police reports into mini podcasts, illustrations, and narrations to make them differently understood and more comprehensive to broader publics. We are mainly interested in exploring what public communication in science and technology offers that other forms of communicating do not.

"Science and Technology in Popular Culture": How Discussions of Representation and Collective Attitudes Influence Engineering Education *Bryn Seabrook*, *University of Virginia*

The field of Science, Technology, and Society (STS) draws from a full range of disciplines in the social sciences and humanities to examine how science and technology simultaneously shape and

are shaped by society, including politics and culture. Although engineering educators and employers have recognized the importance of professional (nontechnical) skills for over 100 years, the instructional strategies and institutional arrangements necessary to help students develop these skills have not yet settled into a widely adopted standard. Many engineering programs have turned to STS to provide students with conceptual tool kits to think about engineering problems and solutions in more sophisticated ways. Some programs feature standalone courses on the sociocultural aspects of technology and engineering, often taught by faculty from outside the engineering school. Others incorporate STS material into traditional engineering courses, e.g., by making ethical or societal impact assessments part of capstone projects. The purpose of this study is to investigate how a new course titled "Science and Technology in Popular Culture" engages with the nontechnical skills required for engineering professionals by examining how stories, images, and works of culture reflect shared beliefs, and how those beliefs influence the work of scientists and engineers. There is a clear need to create spaces where engineering students can freely discuss and understand the nontechnical influences of their profession. Often these conversations are brief, or simply do not exist in current engineering curricula. At the end of a previous course, one student commented, "There has been no instance where I have talked about race in a serious in-depth discussion in any of my engineering classes. Consequently, I can infer that means that none of my peers have either. Nevertheless, the conversation has to be pushed if we're going to get better at making ethical decisions around race." How can the field of STS attend to these issues in order to prepare the engineers of the future? "Science and Technology in Popular Culture" asks engineering students to consider the role of culture and media in engineering. Some of the main questions include: How do representations of scientists and engineers change over time? What patterns emerge? What effect do popular representations have on the working lives of scientists, engineers, or policy makers? This discussion-based course challenges engineering students to think more critically about topics such as global climate change, gender, and race in order to reflect on how the engineering design process integrates the social dimensions of engineering problems.

Who Thinks Science is nothing but an Opinion? Modern-Day Discontents and the Educational Gradient in Epistemological Insecurity *phj achterberg, Tilburg University*

In current debates about post-truthism and the relationship between science and society, the idea that 'science is nothing more than an opinion' plays a prominent role. In this paper, I investigate public support for such claims. More specific in this paper, I study three issues: 1) Whether these epistemologically insecure opinions about scientific knowledge coincide with a broader sense of 'epistemological insecurity' that criticizes all types of institutional knowledge. 2) Whether there are differences between the lower and higher educated in epistemologically insecure attitudes towards science and other institutions alike. And 3) I investigate explanations for such educational differences based on modern-day discontents. I study whether educational differences in alienation – the idea that abstract modern institutions are too controlling – or differences in anomia – the idea that such institutions are meaningless - affect epistemological insecurity. To verify my expectations about epistemological insecurity, I use cross-sectional data (N=1,500) gathered in the Netherlands in 2020. The results point out that those who think science is a matter of opinion also apply this principle to other types of institutional knowledge. I also find that the lower educated are more likely to embrace epistemological insecurity and that this is mainly rooted in alienation, and more strongly in anomia – signaling that science institutions are more forcefully criticized for moral reasons than any other. At the end of the paper, I discuss the theoretical

ramifications of my findings.

Session Organizer:

Barbara Kirsi Silva, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

Chair:

Barbara Kirsi Silva, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

071. Forensic Devices: How They Mediate, How They Are Discussed, How They Mitigate Interprofessional Conflicts - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

The term "forensics" derives from the Latin word "forensis" meaning "belonging to the forum, market (place)". The etymology recalls that court proceedings and investigations are public affairs and so they were often conducted on the Forum in ancient Rome. Following this line of thought, several STS works have depicted how experts present forensic findings in the courtroom, explain their evidence and put them up for evaluation. Recent papers have then turned to the epistemic foundations of forensic science. In our panel we want to take up these discussions and push them in a new direction. For while the relationship between forensics and law is already well studied, the intersections of forensics and the society/public, forensics and basic science, and forensics and the police have hardly been explored so far. We propose to take a closer look at these relations by using the example of forensic devices. By forensic devices we do not only mean machines and tools, but also databases, information technologies, and procedures guiding forensic practices. We are looking for studies dedicated to the social life of forensic devices, to their role as mediators or boundary objects between different areas and fields of practice, as well as the public debate about their trustworthiness, risks and chances. We particularly encourage contributions focussing on how these devices help their users to navigate the gap between – and the quest for loyalty to – the realm of investigation on the one hand and the realm of science on the other.

Participants:

Algorithm as Both Tool and 'Backing': Probabilistic DNA Profiling at the Office of the Chief Medical Examiner *Amy Weissenbach, Columbia University, Department of Sociology; Hannah Pullen-Blasnik, Columbia University; Kiran Samuel, Columbia University; Gil Eyal, Columbia University*

Science scholars have shown that forensic scientists' practices are shaped by the "culture of anticipation" (Bechky 2020), namely awareness of courtroom actors' expectations and demands. Important to this culture is objectivity, and the training, ethical commitments, procedures and workplace routines that increase trust in the objectivity of forensic expertise. One would expect that forensic scientists would be keen to incorporate algorithms into their work processes, as these are typically understood as a form of mechanical objectivity (Porter 1995). We interviewed forensic scientists (specifically, "Criminalists" at an Office of the Chief Medical Examiner) about their experiences working with STRmix, a probabilistic DNA Profiling (PDP) algorithm increasingly used to determine the likelihood that an individual is a "contributor" to a mixed DNA trace. Contrary to our expectations, we find that criminalists tend to downplay the algorithm's role, and especially avoid presenting their assessments as the result of the algorithm's mechanical objectivity. The algorithm has created new sources of ambiguity and potential vulnerability for criminalists. For example, their expert testimony could be challenged on the grounds that they did not reach the conclusion themselves, but rely on an algorithm that they do not quite understand. Hence, they are concerned to frame the significance of the algorithm as merely a "tool." Yet they cannot do without the algorithm and rely upon it to provide them with "statistical backing." We show that forensic scientists have to constantly move back-and-forth between the languages of mechanical objectivity and of expert judgment, without ever quite reconciling them.

Statistical Models and Software as Forensic Devices: Between

Science, Market, and Practice *Simon A Cole, Univ Of Ca-Irvine; Justin Sola, University of California, Irvine*

This paper treats statistical models and associated software as “forensic devices” with the potential to mitigate interprofessional conflicts. Calls for the reform or improvement of forensic science are now entering their fourth decade, and statistics and probability have emerged as potential solutions to the perceived problems inherent in forensic science. Specifically, it has been suggested that these disciplines can help forensic scientists quantify their results and report those results in a logically coherent fashion. At a practical level, these interventions take the form of two kinds of “devices.” First, forensic statisticians have developed statistical models with which to generate quantitative expressions of the value of forensic evidence. Second, at a more practical level, there have been efforts to develop software that would allow these models to be deployed in actual quotidian forensic practice. The most widely discussed of these devices are software packages for “probabilistic genotyping,” the automated interpretation of complex DNA mixtures. Outside of DNA, however, the dissemination and adoption of these devices has made surprisingly slow progress, despite the efforts of various stakeholders. This paper will contribute to STS research on forensic science by exploring why progress has been so slow based on two sources of data: interviews with stakeholders and focus groups within forensic service providers (FSPs). It will argue that these forensic devices have thus far failed to mitigate interprofessional conflicts between the scientists who devise statistical models, the vendors who market software to FSPs, and the bench practitioners who would have to use them.

Techno-Assemblages and Digital Witness Testimony: A New Materialist Approach to Forensic Studies *Alexi Orchard, University of Waterloo*

The introduction of digital evidence to the courtroom has ushered in a new age for forensic investigation. The ever-expanding Internet of Things (IoT) has both simplified and complexified the legal process (Burgess 2018). This paper takes a new materialist approach to a 2018 murder case that was captured by two sources: the victim’s Fitbit fitness watch data and a neighbor’s Ring surveillance camera footage. While the digital evidence was highly incriminating, the victim’s DNA, found in the defendant’s home, was crucial to the verdict (Smiley 2019). These objects might also be considered legal actants, described by Bennett as one that “by virtue of its particular location in an assemblage and the fortuity of being in the right place at the right time... becomes the decisive force catalyzing an event” (2010, p. 9). Taken together as a “digital data assemblage” (Lupton 2015), the Fitbit and Ring data represent discrete flows of information, emerging from the amalgamation of vital materials, and societal apparatuses that permit this narrative to take place. This paper will also consider the relationship between biological evidence and the digital devices within the “surveillant assemblage” (Haggerty and Ericson 2000). I argue that there is less of an ontological tension between the Fitbit, Ring camera, and DNA, and more of a rhetorical exigence that determines what exercises reliability in particular contexts of litigation. Understanding digital data assemblages, as they spread through the IoT, is critical to maintaining legal and public infrastructures as human life becomes more ingrained in sociotechnical entanglements.

Tracing Models: Circulating Reference in Forensic Practice *Nils Ellebrecht, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany; Jan Schank, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, Centre for Security and Society*

The presentation will compare the use of models in two different areas of forensic practice: forensic genetics aiming to relate traces from crime scenes to individuals or “suspect groups” and forensic physics, in our case used to reconstruct explosive devices from traces found at the site of an attack. We start from the observation that, generally, forensic practice aims to

reconstruct past occurrences by relating the traces left at a physical site to scientific models, thus translating them into plausible evidence in and for legal procedure. Accordingly, the aim is to achieve a tripartite relation between physical traces, scientific models, and legal concepts. In the case of forensic genetics, reference databases and statistical methods are used to calculate the “biogeographical ancestry” or the persuasiveness of a “match”, whereas the reconstruction of explosive devices relies on models from physics and engineering. The possibility of scrutiny by the adversary in legal procedure puts some limits on the extend to which these models can remain “black boxes”. Similar to scientific practice, the possibility to ‘open up parts of the black box’ is sustained by a web of “circulating references,” which can (and occasionally will) be re-examined to amplify or reduce the strength of certain connections within that web. Based on interviews and participant observation as well as video data from table-top exercises with forensic experts, the presentation will highlight some of the ways in which these references are established, including attempts to shield those connections from being undone in the subsequent legal procedure.

Session Organizers:

Nils Ellebrecht, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Veronika Lipphardt, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, University College Freiburg

072. Mediation, Probability, and Environmental Risk - II: Environmental Disaster and Media of Anticipation

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

In the third session of the Mediation, Probability, and Environmental Risk stream, participants discuss the role of media technology in informing communities and anticipating environmental risk. These papers will consider in particular the affective experiences of precarity, and the specificity of various media platforms—from maps, to social media, to audio formats—in helping vulnerable communities to anticipate and prepare for climate-change related disasters such as floods and typhoons. These case studies explore how real, past events can educate and inform future behavior, and emphasize the importance of collaborative, community-centered design when it comes to disaster communication and infrastructure. From an examination of uneven risk distributions in flood zones, to a consideration of the affordances of podcasts in fostering environmental awareness, this session directly responds to the conference’s provocation around “Good Relations in Unequal and Uncertain Worlds” by reflecting on how various technologies of mediation have both exacerbated inequalities and facilitated more equitable modes of relation between residents and their homelands.

Participants:

Surviving Typhoons with Disaster Communication

Infrastructure in the Philippines *Shelley Tuazon Guyton*

How do survivors of previous disaster mitigate their risk to future disaster with media? Few studies of analyze peoples’ differing interactions with disaster communication infrastructure that people experience based on their access to media technologies, location, socio-economic status, livelihoods, gender, etc. This paper contributes to STS perspectives on socio-technical relationships of disaster communication infrastructure through the ethnographic perspective. From 2016-2018, I conducted ethnographic fieldwork with residents of a low-income coastal neighborhood in Tacloban City, Philippines. Residents there survived Super-typhoon Yolanda in 2013 in which massive storm surges (tsunami-like waves) destroyed their homes and drowned many loved ones. To ensure they are prepared for the next super-typhoon, residents gather weather updates nearly every day from many different sources (radio, television, social media, etc.) In this paper, I analyze these residents’ experiences with the disaster communication infrastructure, touching upon themes of trust and distrust, scientific literacy, and media technology sharing. I argue

that the most important aspects of disaster communication infrastructure are what happens outside government-structured flows of communication. Disaster alerts take meaning when people talk about them with their family, friends and neighbors. Based on these findings, I advocate that just, affirmative and decolonial experiences of disaster communication infrastructure should include design that is centered on the differing needs of vulnerable populations, and specifically within this direction that disaster communication should be reimagined for its possibilities as multi-directional conversations rather than uni-directional alerting.

The Veneer of Certitude: Redrawing the Nature and Culture of Risk in New Orleans *Martin Abbott, Cornell University*

At the stroke of midnight on September 30, 2016, the Flood Insurance Rate Map (FIRM) of New Orleans was instantly redrawn. Barely a decade after Hurricane Katrina flooded 80 percent of the city and in defiance of the rising risks posed by climate change, the new map suggested that much of the city was now safe from flooding. The implications of changing this technopolitical map are profound because FIRMs are crucial components of the federal government's trillion-dollar National Flood Insurance Program. As the new FIRM came into effect, experts and journalists scrutinized the technical basis of FEMA's reassessment process. This sudden media interest, however, belies a ten-year reassessment process that welcomed local government intervention on three occasions. In contradistinction to what city officials espouse publicly, the same officials also privately acknowledge that a map cannot represent the dynamic environmental reality confronting the city. The cartographic certainty these maps present offers only a veneer of certitude. In this paper, I show how these modes of calculation shape uneven risk burdens, with implications for environmental equity and justice within New Orleans. To unpack these burdens, I chart the controversy surrounding the new FIRM and show how technologies of quantification and their cartographic representation are redrawing environmental risk in New Orleans. Drawing on Beck's risk society theory, I also consider how climate change reorders the practice of urban planning for equitable and just futures in New Orleans.

Podcasts: more people are listening, are more people paying attention? *Amy Harris, SFU*

The rise of podcasts in recent years has been almost exponential; 2020 statistics show that 36% of all Canadians are now monthly listeners (Edison, 2019). Of those podcasts available, there are many that tackle the issue of climate change and environmental risk. These podcasts aim to educate listeners, and often claim that through exploration of relevant topics, that they can change the behaviour of listeners to take more action to mitigate the risks of climate change. But how effective are they? What impact do they have? And are they reaching the audiences necessary to enact real change? By focusing on some of the most popular podcasts on climate change in Canada: CBC's 2050: Degrees of Change; Crude; and Simply Science, this study seeks to gain an understanding of how these shows impact listeners' behaviour, and potentially, how they could do more. Using fundamental theory from Horkheimer & Adorno (2002), to modern analysis of apathy and stuplidity from Sianne Ngai (2004), this study will firstly provide a media history of podcasting in Canada. Further, following Fernandez et al (2017), analysis of Twitter data from users who follow these podcasts will be analysed using to determine awareness of risk, and if correlation can be detected between listening and behavioural change. Podcasts are often seen as mechanisms for increasing connections with their familiar and conversational tone, but do these 'good relations' have an impact on practice of their listeners? Let's find out.

Session Organizer:

Amy Harris, SFU

Discussant:

Thomas Patrick Pringle, Tulane University

073. Mapping the Conceptual Vocabulary of AI in the Global South - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

The possibilities of leveraging Big Data through AI-based interventions are often poised to flow as innovations emerging from the Global North as the active center to the Global South as the passive periphery. Problematizing these flows, this panel is oriented towards showcasing that the Global South is neither a passive recipient, nor is it the periphery of these innovations. The panel invites submissions that identify new and/or reinterpret old concepts and keywords that underlie the emerging meaning(s) and future(s) of AI in the Global South. The range of conversations on this topic operates on a wide spectrum between optimism of leapfrogging and digital transformation of societies on one end and the pessimism of human suffering caused by new forms of data capitalism and colonialism on the other. Mapping this spectrum, the members of this panel will not only present their concepts, keywords, research methods, and case studies in understanding the building and consequences of these technologies, but also collaboratively engage with each other in developing a broader conceptual vocabulary of AI in the Global South. The panel asks what stories of AI are told and shared, what unequal and uncertain world(s) do these stories build, what hopes and concerns do they amplify, and what future(s) do they imagine in the Global South. After all, the concepts and keywords to describe the mutual shaping of AI and society have different intellectual trajectories in different parts of the world. Recognizing this difference is the first step towards understanding it.

Participants:

Counting on Good Relations: Transport Platform Companies in Beijing *Thea Marie Valler, Norwegian University of Science & Technology (NTNU)*

Platform companies that offer on-demand transport services have become an integral part of Chinese cities. Dockless bikes and food delivery services have considerably changed the color pallet of cities across the country. However, together with the less visible ride-hailing services, they have also spurred public anger and caused regulatory headaches for authorities. These platform companies thus need to secure good relations with the government, particularly at the local level. One way they do so is by providing services, such as transport data and ICT expertise. Although these companies are not part of smart city projects per se, they still contribute to the 'smartification' of urban governance. However, the data provided by platform companies does not capture the whole population as they require a smartphone. While it is uncertain how data from platform companies impact urban planning, it is clear that some groups are better represented in the data than others. For example, young men are disproportionately the users of dockless bikes. Simultaneously, as some platform companies are lobbying for better bicycle infrastructure, there might also be more promising aspects of such cooperation. This paper builds on fieldwork in Beijing, which focused on ride-hailing and dockless bike services. To shed light on these issues, I will draw on the New Mobilities Paradigm, the Sustainability transitions literature, and insights from theories on Chinese policymaking. Overall, I seek to contribute to discussions on relations both between technology companies and the government, and data and urban infrastructure.

The Social Networks and Data Annotation in Latin America *Julian Posada, University of Toronto*

Firms and research organizations require humans to annotate raw data to make it compatible with machine learning algorithms. These tasks are often outsourced to individuals worldwide through crowdsourcing platforms or infrastructures that serve as marketplaces where labour is exchanged as a commodity. The firms that operate them consider workers as "independent contractors" without the social and economic benefits of

traditional employment relations. This presentation explores the personal networks of Latin American “crowdworkers” who train and verify artificial intelligence systems from their homes. A series of in-depth interviews and an analysis of online forums suggests that these workers are embedded in networks of trusts build on online and offline interactions. While research focused on anglophone platform workers suggests that most of their networks related to this type of work depend exclusively on online forums, those of Latin American workers receive support from their families and close relations who provide financial, emotional, and technical support. This presentation concludes by arguing that, though outsourced online labour, artificial intelligence developers not only extract value from their workers, but also indirectly from their communities and personal networks.

XML Workers: The Hidden Actors of Scholarly Communication in Mexico *NESTOR DANIEL DOMINGUEZ, Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana-Azcapotzalco, México*

One of the main trends in scholarly communication is the digitization of editorial processes and the contents of books and scientific journals. For the science system, the digital native edition represents the possibility of interoperability between different scientific databases and that the contents circulate more efficiently on the internet and can be consumed by wider audiences. Thus, data and metadata are currently the “black gold” in scientific publication because apart from their informative uses, they also serve to generate indicators of scientific production. However, to achieve this, specialized human resources in data mining, machine learning and artificial intelligence are needed that, in many countries of the global south, are not found within the editorial teams, which are produced in universities, which must hire companies to carry out this work. The main of this paper is to present some preliminary results of my doctoral research on how companies specializing in markup XML (Extensible Markup Language) begin to reconfigure and have a sociotechnical agency in the landscape of scientific publishing in Mexico, a country that has changed since 2016 its public policy instruments for financial support for the publication of scientific journals, which can be spent on the production of XML, a phenomenon that points to a sociotechnical division of scholarly publishing work and the need to propose clear accountability systems for this activity carried out by humans and machines that, although they are not part of the scientific collectives, are beginning to be important actors for the circulation of scientific knowledge.

Session Organizer:

Ranjit Pal Singh, Data & Society Research Institute

Chair:

Noopur Raval

Discussant:

Rida Qadri, MIT

074. Markets as data - III - Standards and Market Infrastructures

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

STS scholars have long been interested in the diverse devices that equip markets, from market infrastructures to mundane marketing tools such as shopping carts, knowledge devices, and measuring instruments. As markets are digitized, consumer records, scoring and targeting instruments, trading machines, and so on are key to how markets operate. Data act as a versatile, yet vital, apparatus for markets, playing crucial roles in the form of devices, valuation tools, infrastructures, and assets. This panel will explore these various facets of data, and how they help to bring markets into being. We welcome empirical and theoretical investigations of markets as data. First, with big data technologies, marketing knowledge is increasingly produced from the analysis of large databases that combine heterogeneous arrays of

information on consumers, products, firms, and market operations. These data are then stabilized through metrics, dashboards and standards. How do these new “data objects” and knowledge devices reconfigure practices? Second, data streams are fueling automation or decision-making systems: matching algorithms, trade desks, recommendation engines, smart contracts, market screening mechanisms, dashboards. How does automation reconfigure firms’ practices in markets? Third, data are increasingly marketized themselves, harvested from public-facing services such as social media. How do markets for data impact “conventional” markets? Finally, data practices are increasingly subject to specific governance that is often the object of fierce contestation: from regulation such as GDPR in Europe, industry-level self-regulation and labelling processes, to local framing within firms. How does the governance of data, and its contestation shape markets and marketization practices?

Participants:

Market Metadata: ANNA and the uneven infrastructures of financial assetization *Ulysses Pascal, Department of Information Studies, UCLA*

Before assets can be traded on global, digitized marketplaces they have to be defined. As Birch and Munisea (2020) argue, assets are not given, they are constructed through socio-technical processes. Financial assets are social-technically constructed through the production of metadata standards. In information management systems, metadata schema are high levels of abstraction that formally represent entities and possible relationships in specific domains (Pomerantz 2015). Standards such as ISIN (ISO 6166), CFI (ISO 10962), MIC (ISO 10383), FISN (ISO 18774) and LEI (ISO 17442) describe the numbering algorithms used to generate codes that classify and uniquely identify securities in order to facilitate international transactions. The Association of National Numbering Agencies (ANNA) is the organization responsible for codifying, implementing, and maintaining the metadata standards that represent financial asset classes such as bonds, stocks, derivatives and other securities. Comprised of member banks, securities exchanges, clearing houses, and other financial institutions, ANNA’s role is manage the assignment of unique International Securities Identification Numbers (ISINs) to globally tradable securities. To ensure that all countries are integrated to digitized financial infrastructures, all countries either operate their own national numbering agency or work with a one of four numbering agencies headquartered in the Global North. This analysis of ANNA members (n=254), traces the infrastructural power of metadata schema in globalized finance with quantitative and qualitative methods. Despite performances of globalness, ANNA remains regionally controlled by European and American institutions.

Monetizing the Social: Exploring the Devices and Valuation Infrastructures of the Influencer Marketing Industry *Thomas W.L. MacDonald, Queen's University*

As of early 2021, industry blogs estimate that over 1,380 influencer marketing platforms were in operation. As aspiring market infrastructures for an enormous digital marketing industry, these platforms draw together vast amounts of social media data to produce data analytics, capitalize on this knowledge, and coordinate the economic activities of actors in the market for social media influence. Unlike the monetization systems of social media platforms like YouTube, Facebook, or Instagram—which assess viewing behaviors to algorithmically allocate advertisements—these monetization systems leverage the ‘authenticity’ of the relationship between influencers, social media users, and commercial brands. In this paper, I draw on STS scholarship on markets and infrastructures to explore how influencer marketing platforms monetize the social. How do their sociotechnical devices—their interfaces, metrics, and monetization models—construct labour and goods markets for social media influencers and their content? How are their infrastructures influenced by existing standards from legacy media industries and emerging ones from the gig economy? To

answer these questions, I employ a walkthrough analysis of five influencer marketing platforms to contribute empirical and theoretical insights into the sociotechnical translation of social relationships into metrics and data analytics, and how intermediary platforms in the digital marketing sector construct and stabilize markets for influence.

Is data enough to evaluate influence? The birth and evolution of a measurement industry *Ms M. Valeria Ramirez, Universite Gustave Eiffel - LISIS - CONACYT*

Public Relations (PR) practitioners have traditionally been reluctant to use quantitative evaluation. Their professional values are rooted in an instinctive deeper knowledge of the audiences and their expertise relies on personal influence. However, while most of the practitioners distrusted communication measuring instruments and rejected advertising metrics like exposure, a professional mobilisation discreetly started to germinate. To what extent social media data allowed for this happen? A segment (Bucher and Strauss, 1961) explored the possibilities offered by technologies as early as 1990. These pioneers developed computer programs to automatise media content analysis. The display of rudimentary media listening devices allowed for a new industry to dawn. In 1996 the UK trade Association for the Measurement and Evaluation of Communication (AMEC) was born. But it was not until 2010 when, pulled by the explosion of social media metrics, that the association and the industry got international notoriety. By this time, they had renewed their purpose. While relying on technology and integrating the values of the profession, they gave themselves the mission to question technological innovation of data markets to “measure and evaluate communication with metrics that make sense”.

Audience data has been used as currency (Kosterich and Napoli, 2016; Méadel, 2010; Napoli, 2010) but there are yet other uses to explore. Aided by a corpus of semi structured interviews, press and trade documents, this research study the industry dynamics and discourses in an effort to provide an account of a parallel measurement data industry, their conventions and struggles in order to exist.

The standard story of SAP: When infrastructure is happening *Lisa Conrad, Leuphana Universität Lüneburg*

This paper tells the standard story of SAP, thus how the software manufacturer managed to provide today’s standard tool of organization. While prompted and flanked by the authors’ extensive empirical engagement with SAP, it draws on a broad collection of secondary sources, such as published interviews with SAP’s founders and historical research on business software. In order to comb through the complex history of SAP from its beginning in the 1970s until the 2010s, we focus on key concepts from the field of infrastructure studies. This means, amongst other things, to distinguish different phases of the standard: 1) in the making, 2) in action, and 3) in circulation. We show how SAP managed to create a standard, how it turned into a de facto standard and how it dealt with newly emerging standards related to the internet. All in all, we show that contingencies related to the dynamics of standards have crucially shaped the development of SAP. Throughout its history, it acted around the happening of infrastructure.

Platformization and Big Tech in the Construction Industry: The Political Techno-Economy of Building Information Modeling *Kathrin Braun; Cordula Kropp, University of Stuttgart; Yana Boeva, University of Stuttgart*

Big Tech’s proliferation is reaching architecture, engineering, and construction (AEC). While AEC has been reluctant about adopting digital technologies, digitalization is fueling the expectations of increased productivity and efficiency, integrated forms of data processing, and automated construction. Building Information Modeling (BIM) plays a central role in these expectations. BIM designates the digital convergence of a 3D building model, a database including information on geometry,

components, costs, and an interface for multidisciplinary collaboration. The global BIM market, concerning software, standards, and data integration, is dominated by the leading software company Autodesk and its BIM product Revit. Autodesk has secured a hegemonic position through digital networks, subscription models, and governmental support. Big Tech in the face of Autodesk and Revit defines digital formats, interfaces, and standards for building models and the possible datafication and assetization of their contents. We argue that BIM’s political and techno-economic configuration as a Big Tech project underpins a near-monopolistic platform structure creating new constraints and implications for AEC’s future and the built environment. The paper examines the digitalization of the AEC markets with Big Tech’s impact on it from the perspectives of digital platform capitalism (Smrcek 2017; Staab, 2020), technoscientific capitalism (Birch, 2020), and assetization studies (Birch and Muniesa, 2020), focusing on the co-production and intersection of technical, political, and economic drivers. We draw on interviews with AEC professionals along with a document analysis on the digital transformation of architecture and construction.

Session Organizers:

Thomas Beauvisage, Orange Labs
Donald MacKenzie, University Of Edinburgh
Kevin Mellet, Sciences Po - CSO
Zsuzsanna Vargha, ESCP Business School

Chair:

Thomas Beauvisage, Orange Labs

075. Pandemic Breathing – Air as Matter of Dis/Connection II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

In times of the covid-19-pandemic air becomes an element known for its aerosols being capable of passing a virus mouth-to-mouth. It is obvious that air is an element of connection, an interface where humans and more-than-humans, bodies and the world interfere (cf. Adey 2014, Allen 2020, Baake 2018, Görská 2016). Air is pure complexity: it is full of relations, it is a microcosm composed of heterogeneous elements. But air is also a boundless matter difficult to discipline. During the pandemic human breathing has become a matter of disconnecting physical bodies that should keep a distance measured in meters or whose exhalations should only meet filtered by a mask. But what happens in filtering practices and can they be studied as a nature-culture separation processes? Moreover, ‘[a]ll air is not equal’ (Godfrey & Torres, 2016: 9), since the air in urban areas is polluted, not everyone can afford ventilation systems or simply because lung volumes vary. The corona crisis has exposed the socio-spatial, political and economic aspects of breathing. It changes our thoughtless relationship with the air and is a burning lens that makes both microscopic connections and dis-connections visible. With our talk we would like to discuss this double character of air using various examples.

Participants:

Suspension in the virosphere: Breathing in hotel quarantine
Michele Lobo, Deakin University; Kaya Barry, Griffith University

This paper introduces and develops the concept of the virosphere by focusing on Australian cities during the Covid-19 pandemic. We draw on interviews, photographs, videos, sketches and journal reflections from returning travellers in 2020/2021 who spent a fortnight in mandatory hotel quarantine. Their encounters with airflow, light, dust, noise, cityscape views, material objects, masked bodies and the invisible SARS-CoV-2 provides insights into distributed agency and the affective dimensions of the virosphere. Rather than merely diagrams of ‘command and control’, quarantine hotels emerge as places with co-existing atmospheres that facilitate as well hamper pandemic breathing. The paper draws attention to the sociomateriality of breathing regulated by biopolitical frameworks that attempt to govern human-virus encounters but often fails because of

anthropocentric frames. We argue that these pandemic border infrastructures and places of governed containment are disrupted by body–viral–spheres in an impasse or ‘a space of time lived without a narrative genre’ (Berlant, 2011). We show that it is shared suspension in the virosphere that produces dis/connections with the materiality of the air amid bioinsecurities of the pandemic.

Elevators and healthy relations: Building knowledge about breathing and vertical dis/connections during the Corona pandemic *Robert Stock, Humboldt Universität zu Berlin*
Take the stairs and not the elevator. This well-known motto suggests that movement promotes health. However, it should be treated with caution. Office employees require fast elevators. Freight lifts spare the bodies of deliverers. People with walkers, wheelchairs or prams should be able to take the elevator instead of the stairs. However, elevator practices (Hirschauer2005) entered a state of crisis, when the Corona virus began to affect the good—and often uneven—relations of vertical mobility (Graham2016). The elevator became a target of regulatory measures concerning the physical distancing of passengers, hygienic measures of operating panels and the introduction of intelligent air purification systems. Against this background, my talk examines epistemic practices for creating a healthy vertical microclimate during the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic. First, these air-related practices can be located on the side of health authorities and associations such as the National Elevator Industry Inc., which establish hygienic standards based on scientific studies. Second, manufacturers (Thyssen/Krupp) build engineering knowledge and design new air filtration systems. Thirdly, improvised pandemic adaptations, new standards and innovation-oriented materials design intersect in the socio-technical assemblages of the elevator as an element of digital media infrastructure spaces (Easterling2014) enacting heterogeneous users, inequalities and novel daily practices that dis/able access. I conceive this field of action as an exemplary site to study the pandemic “politics and sociomateriality of breathing” by using various material from manufacturers, health authorities and user reports (blogs) and hence connecting STS, cultural studies of knowledge and critical media access studies (Alper2021).

... to **Ashes and Dust: Cremation, Air Quality, and the Unclaimed Dead** *Lee Nelson*

In 2020, hospitals, funeral homes, and crematoria in Los Angeles were running out of space to store the deceased due to the number of deaths due to Covid, the fiscal and legal limitations on families’ ability to recover their loved ones’ remains for burial, and air quality policy. Because of historic air quality issues in Los Angeles, in 1976 the South Coast Air Quality Management District was established to regulate stationary sources of air pollution, one of which was crematoria. In response to the bottleneck produced by Covid deaths, limited storage capacity, and the number of cremations were temporarily suspended on January 17th for Los Angeles County. The suspension was subsequently renewed for Los Angeles County and expanded to Orange County and Riverside County until March 4th. These events occurred amidst a more diffuse history of air, pollution, and class. In times of monetary hardship, the number of unclaimed bodies increases due to the inability of family to pay for the recovery and funeral of their loved ones. This being the case, the unclaimed are most often from impoverished communities. This talk will examine the regulatory frameworks of cremation in relation to air quality, air quality’s relation to class, and the class relationship to the cremation of the unclaimed. Through an analysis of the temporary regulatory air quality suspensions of January 2020 Los Angeles, a story unfolds of ‘air after the last breath’ that preexisted and will ‘outlive’ Covid’s American presence.

The Politics and Perceptibility of Breath During the COVID-19

Pandemic *Vaibhavi Shah, MIT*

Despite the changes brought about during the COVID-19 pandemic, there was a central consistency: a renewed focus on the air that we breathe. Around the world, the importance of breathing has become a focus of social, political, and technical debate. Our right to breathe has been treated as a physical artifact that can be regulated. Instead of remaining an invisible process, instinctual and otherwise unimportant, breathing has become a conscious action fraught with consequence. This paper explores, through a case study approach, the politics of breath in relation to historical parallels in the United States where breath has been at the forefront of conversations. The pertinent themes are how breath shifted from a pure to a dangerous force, from an intangible to a tangible object of conversation, and from a communal to an individualized commodity. The first case study explores indoor spaces that have harbored “dangerous air”, from sick buildings to academic institutions. The second section explores inequities in access to clean air as it relates to environmental justice, civil rights, and “I Can’t Breathe” protests in 2020. The last case study centers around the individualization of breath in the regulatory landscape of secondhand smoke and anti-mask sentiment. The spotlight on breath in the United States throughout this paper provides a crucial launching point for discussion. Particularly, was this emphasis on breath and related political discourse, evident in other nations during the pandemic? This exploration can provide an expansion of what we consider to be the “society” element of STS.

Breathing in the (Viral) Wake: Between Exploitation and Aspiration during the Novel Coronavirus *Joshua Falek, York University; Patrick Teed, York University*

As COVID-19 spread across the globe, another aspirational fissure became brutally apparent. On May 25th, 2020, Derek Chauvin, a white police officer, knelt on George Floyd’s neck for eight minutes, murdering the 46-year-old Black man for the alleged exchange of a counterfeit \$20 bill outside Cup Foods in Minneapolis, Minnesota. Many political critics and activists were quick to point out how Floyd’s articulation of “I can’t breathe” resonated across the decade as emblematic of rather than exceptional to the condition of Black life today. Indeed, the reiterability of “I can’t breathe” marks an aspirational precarity that precedes and exceeds the aspirational precarity induced by the novel coronavirus. In this paper and in conversation with scholars like Christina Sharpe, Dionne Brand, Jared Sexton, Frank Wilderson, and Katherine McKittrick, we argue through an Afro-pessimist analysis that a condition of breathlessness is actually the (non)ontology of Black life. Given this aspirational precarity that circumscribes Black life—as evidenced by recent discourse framing police violence and anti-Black racism as the “second pandemic” Black people face—we contend that the ‘crisis’ of the novel coronavirus might be an imperfect elaboration of the political ontology of Black life in the wake, which is to say life for which breath is not (a) given. This paper concludes by thinking about Rinaldo Walcott’s provocation that abolition is another name for “the route to Black people’s full breath,” to question what an abolition might offer Science and Technology Studies, potentially reorienting theorizations of care, being and freedom.

Session Organizers:

Lisa Wiedemann, Helmut Schmidt University Hamburg
Vanessa Weber, HafenCity University

Chairs:

Lisa Wiedemann, Helmut Schmidt University Hamburg
Vanessa Weber, HafenCity University

076. Practices And Methods Towards Good Relations With Robots And AI III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Participants:

Drawn into the Future. The Epistemic Work Visual Scenarios Do in Configuring Human-Machine Encounters *Christian Pentzold, University of Leipzig; Ingmar Rothe, Leipzig University*

In our paper, we take a close look at artistic impressions of future robotics and how they come to inspire actual research around human-machine interaction. The images envision highly artificial scenes crowded with encounters between many kinds of embodied digital technologies (EDTs) and humans from all walks of life. While being genuinely out-of-touch with what is currently possible for engineering and implementation, the visuals are taken to give visual form to expectations and aspirations around EDTs. We examine the career of what we define as visual scenarios whose diegetic futurescapes are imaginatively engaging and imbue scientific progress and experimenting. The analysis emerges from our involvement in a Collaborative Research Center (CRC) funded by the German Research Foundation (DFG). The multi-disciplinary research endeavor brings together more than 100 researchers in order to advance the implementation of EDTs in public spaces. Within the ongoing CRC, we are both active members managing science communications and participant observers reflecting on the epistemic work done at these interfaces. Here, the register of evaluation shifted from aesthetic criteria to scientific parameters so to project the speculative scenarios onto the CRC's aims and intention. The drawn accounts thus escape notions of post hoc representation but were taken to be ex ante representative of the ambitions around crafting human-machine relations. Next to drawing it into the future, the scenarios also became an instrument for drawing the large-scale venture together. More than being mere visual tokens, the visual scenarios hence became a catalyst upon which they CRC gained its profile.

Tracing Imaginaries Of Healthcare Robotics and AI Through EU Public Policy *Svenja Breuer, Munich Center for Technology in Society (MCTS); Ruth Müller, MCTS TU München*

The integration of robotics and artificial intelligence (AI) into healthcare and medicine promises significant transformations in healthcare practice. For example, they change the task and skills profiles of healthcare practitioners and mediate interactions between practitioners and patients. Alongside increasing efforts in AI and robotics research for healthcare, we also see an increasing public policy discourse. Policy makers are important actors in this context, because, through their narratives and initiatives, they set out to determine what kinds of knowledges, practices and relations we pursue through innovation in healthcare robotics and AI, simultaneously imagining pathways and creating the spaces to realize these visions. In our work, we emphasize the co-production of healthcare robotics/AI and EU and national healthcare policy, tracing imaginaries of healthcare robotics and AI through public policy documents. In our analysis, we specifically focus on how development and implementation practice is imagined. We analyze how relationships between healthcare practitioners, patients, and machines are envisioned, and how these are imagined to be realized in development practice. As we explore the particular normative, political, and practical implications of EU and German national public policy perspectives – including their ecosystematic perspective on AI innovation, their emphasis on translating AI and robotics research into healthcare practice and the aspirations to digitally network health research and healthcare practice through open data exchange and AI – we argue that the public policy sphere makes an interesting site to study the emergence of new relations between machines and humans in healthcare.

When an old idea meets current struggling: concept of euthyphronicus (eutyfronika) as an answer to the potential technological threats *Anna Adamowicz, Institute of*

Philosophy, Adam Mickiewicz University

The idea of euthyphronicus (eutyfronika) is an original ethical and philosophical concept developed in early 70^s by Polish philosopher of technology Józef Bańka, as his own presumption of how humans should take care of themselves in the modern world determined by rise of emerging technologies. Being a part of so called „Polish School Of Praxeology” (within T. Kotarbiński, S. Lem and others), the notion is a word cluster of Greek origin: euthyphron - a straightforward (hu)man and technics, used in non Anglo-Saxon context to describe both the technical area of modern civilisation and technology as political and social matter. Bańka's concept did not really gain recognition in his own times and philosophical and scientific communities, due to its extremely specific, futuristic and extraordinary character. I would like to present his conception in the context of the development of current technologies such as AI, robotics and Big Data. A fundamental claiming in Bańka's ethical concept is the assumption that all humans share some „natural” and immanent straightforwardness that, according to him, is the most important factor for human well-being. Thus, the goal of euthyphronicus is to elaborate how to protect humans from the potential harmful results of emerging technologies. In my presentation I would like to reflect on the adequacy of that theory in current philosophy of technology and STS. I will try to answer if those kinds of „archofuturistic” methodologies can provide some new perspective on today's technological struggling and what kind of scientific benefits can be brought from them the STS researchers.

Session Organizers:

*Andreas Bischof, University of Technology Chemnitz
Arne Maibaum, TU Berlin*

077. Mass-Produced Uncertainties

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

Participants:

Aiming for Certainty. Corporeal Surprises in Body Work with Exoskeletons *Denisa Butnaru, University of Konstanz*

Exoskeletons are very recent technologies, currently developed for three fields of application: rehabilitation, industry and military. Whereas on the one hand the conception of these gadgets implies replicability, constant testing and measuring of human bodies, on the other hand, they need to precisely respond to the variety and spontaneity of these same bodies. Exoskeletons find themselves embedded in an epistemological conflict, that frames corporeal realities. Because exoskeletons are themselves work in progress, so are the bodies of their users. As a consequence, the forms of body work emerging in the three fields for which these devices are developed oscillate between temporary ability for impaired people, or too-ability for able ones, as those working in industry or military applications. However, both of these corpo-technological achievements need to be understood as sequential, as well as timescape and often taskscape determined. Aiming for certainty in body work with exoskeletons implies very often coping with corporeal surprises. Relying on the heritage of the phenomenology of the body (Maurice Merleau-Ponty [2012] 1945), my intention is in this presentation to discuss the forms of body work (Gimlin 2002; 2007) that contribute to individualize first the body as a scientific object, the body replicable in the device and by the device, and second the body as a subject and thus as a source of spontaneity and as an “uncertain” field of possibilities. To do so, I will use empirical qualitative material (expert and narrative interviews and ethnography).

Governing radical uncertainty in the french nuclear industry *Maël Goumri, CERMES3 INSERM U988*

Nuclear power has developed with the promise of safe operation. In particular, the risk of core meltdown was excluded from

possible accidents in the 60s until the late 90s. Yet faced with a lack of knowledge and incomplete knowledge (Douglas 1995), engineers made many design choices without knowing everything about the risks they were dealing with. This presentation looks at how French nuclear engineers tried to make the nuclear accident impossible despite the lack of knowledge. This presentation argues that in the face of the lack of knowledge, engineers framed the problem of the accident in such a way that it could be technically treatable. This framing is based on the idea that the improvement of knowledge in the future would make it possible to improve the technical mastery of nuclear energy. My presentation shows that the government of radical uncertainty requires an articulation of material practices, knowledge and political choices that forms a "nuclear safety infrastructure" to prevent the nuclear major accident. This presentation is based on 3 years of historical work carried out within the French Nuclear Safety Agency. It mobilises archive data and interviews to understand how engineers have resolved insoluble technical issues.

Randomized Field Experiments and the Uncertain Power of Evidence *Fiona Gedeon Achi; Adrian Wilson, University of California, Berkeley*

The last decades have witnessed the growth of "evidence-based development": a movement to produce "rigorous" evidence about the effectiveness of anti-poverty programs — evidence which can then be used to shape efficient and effective development policy. Philosophically, this movement frames itself as a pragmatic and "agnostic" search for "what works to alleviate poverty"; methodologically, this movement centers on large-scale randomized field experiments as the preferred knowledge-production tool. During the course of our fieldwork at evidence-based development organizations in the U.S., Kenya, and India, the discussions and practices of our interlocutors evinced both their faith in the power of rigorously and scientifically produced evidence and their fears of the uncertain (and limited?) power of that evidence to in fact shape the world. In this paper, we explore the relationship between evidence and impact in evidence-based development research, and the ways in which this evidence-to-impact process relates to our interlocutors' understandings of concepts such as truth, (un) certainty, bias, and generalizability. How do these practitioners of evidence-based-development talk about the 'power' of scientific evidence? What are the utopian imaginaries that they attach to that power? And how do they grapple with the ways in which those utopian imaginaries collide with the disappointing realities of political practice?

Simulating Aging, Feeling Population *Yifan Wang, Rice University*

This paper looks at how simulation exercises are mobilized to generate tangible knowledge of population aging in contemporary China. In particular, by situating practices of aging simulation between the demographic present and future, I show how simulation, though predominantly perceived as an embodied experience located in the individual, becomes a device of mass sensitization of the demographic crisis to come. I explore how simulation exercises make the uncertainties of an aging future relevant to people across generations, and all the same time prompt new ways of relating to the population. This paper is part of my dissertation project on population aging and the industrialization of eldercare in urban China. In the past decade, China's demography has undergone a drastic transformation, while the conceptualization of the population shifted from a concern of overpopulation to population aging. Here I analyze two instances where aging simulation exercises were adopted—successfully or not—as a crucial device of sensibility-making. One case is from a popular Chinese reality TV show while the other from my fieldwork conducted in an eldercare company in Nanjing. This paper will bring together the literature on simulation in disability studies, critical gerontology, and anthropological scholarship in science and technology studies by

examining how the technologies of simulation design are mobilized and circulated in the world.

Unequal Power Relations in Uncertain Situations: Graduate Student Experiences of Irreproducibility *Nicole C Nelson, University of Wisconsin Madison; Raphael Ellis, University of Wisconsin--Madison*

Classic STS analyses of irreproducibility have focused on situations involving high-status actors where the truth of a narrowly defined finding is at stake. Harry Collins's study of gravitational waves, for example, described interactions between established scientists debating whether they had successfully detected gravitational waves. But as David Peterson and Aaron Panofsky point out, most replications are "integrative" rather than "diagnostic"—that is, they are not adjudications on the truth of a finding but pragmatic attempts to integrate a finding into ongoing scientific projects. This paper examines the experiences of graduate students who have experienced a failure to replicate in the course of their everyday scientific work. We surveyed 80 students in the biomedical sciences and conducted semi-structured interviews with 38 of these students about their personal experience with irreproducibility. As in Collins's work, we find that ambiguity and uncertainty are prominent features of these experiences—it is typically unclear whether the failure to replicate lies with the equipment, the experimenter, or the original result. But unlike Collins's case, we find that graduate students overwhelmingly tend to resolve this uncertainty by attributing the failure to their own lack of skill. These everyday replications are diagnostic but in a different sense: they act as referenda on graduate students' skills. Our research therefore demonstrates how ideals of certainty and reproducibility in science are maintained through power differentials between the graduate students who typically experience irreproducibility and their advisors and the scientific literature. This dynamic both inflates scientific certainty and diminishes graduate student well-being.

Session Organizer:

Rebecca R Henderson, University of Florida

Chair:

Laurin Baumgardt, Rice University

078. Computational Media Technologies: Computing and Critique Beyond Disciplinary Configurations - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Despite the ongoing interest in the history, epistemology, sociology, and cultures of computing and its defining practices (see Benjamin 2019, Mackenzie 2001, Roberge & Castelle 2020), the study of computational media remains largely dispersed across a wide range of discipline specific venues. Inspired by the more systemic examinations of computing advanced by fields like critical AI studies, indigenous STS, and media anthropology, however, this open panel brings together scholars who share a similar interest in understanding the transdisciplinary complexities, alternative histories, and political a priori behind computational media. With that intention in mind, we propose to consider computation as a paradigmatic 'media technology' whose entanglement with questions of both mediation and technoscience promises to renew the study of technical cultures at large. Computational media, we contend, provides a rich, boundary (defying) object around which the disciplinary perspective of media studies, history of technology, and science studies can be made to converge. Not only does computational media relate contemporary technoscience to the cybernetic and cyborgial origins of computing (see Haraway 1985, Hayles 1999, Medina 2011), it also forces us to consider mediation as a structuring principle of technoscientific cultures, practices, and epistemologies (see Kittler 1986, Chun 2011). To explore these questions, this open panel will stage a number of interdisciplinary conversations which will not only revisit dominant discourses surrounding the study of computational media, but also challenge the disciplinary frameworks in which they have been historically concentrated.

Participants:

Examining Race and Class Bias in Bail and Predictive Policing

Software: Anti-Racist Critical Code Studies: *Mark C. Marino, University of Southern California; Jeremy Douglass, UC Santa Barbara; Sarah Ciston, University of Southern California; Zachary M Mann*

After another year of excessive police violence against Black lives in the United States, Anti-Racist scholars have interrogated the ways software facilitates and supports an inequitable prison industrial complex. Scholars such as Ruha Benjamin (2019), Meredith Broussard (2019), and others point out how police have harnessed machine learning and artificial intelligence in so-called “predictive policing” algorithms to predict and prevent crime. However, in practice, such software tends to reinforce biased assumptions while seeming to abdicate human prejudice from the equation. Similarly, in the name of reducing court workloads and establishing a fair mechanism for adjudication, bail-setting algorithms further reify these discriminatory practices. In this paper, using the techniques of critical code studies (CCS, Marino 2020) and building on the work of the 2021 CCS Anti-Racist Reading Group, we explore the workings of this software and the ways in which the systems reinforce bias. While the study of artificial intelligence has historically been within the purview of computer science, CCS brings an assemblage of historical, semiotic, sociological, legal, and ethical analysis. CCS names an interdisciplinary approach to close reading computer source code with an eye toward STS, combining historical context, ethnography, and other heuristics. Applying this interdisciplinary approach to the study of AI algorithm code opens an opportunity to intervene in this software abdication. Rather than accept the black box of code as the software equivalent to “blind justice,” this paper will consider assignment of weighted bias as an operational component in the software of “law and order.”

Soft Skills, Hard Work: Training Emotional Labor Online

Annika Butler-Wall

The “affective turn” in critical theory has been central to understanding our embodied entanglements with computational media. Scholars such as Mark Hansen (2004) and Steven Shaviro (2010) have theorized affect in relation to pre-subjective, bodily engagement with new media while others have drawn attention to technologies such as sentiment mining as forms of biopolitical control (Clough 2008, Andrejevic 2011). This paper offers a departure from these frameworks by approaching computational media and affect from a different theoretical genealogy: the feminist sociological study of emotional labor (Hochschild 1983). Over the twentieth century, labor management philosophy shifted from scientific management to what Heather Hicks (2009) calls the “culture of soft work” in which feminized “soft skills” like emotion management became valued by corporations. Today, digital technologies have provided new opportunities for codifying these skills through eLearning tools. Drawing on feminist STS frameworks such as Melissa Gregg’s (2018) research on technologies of “mindful labor” and Judy Wajeman’s (1998) study of gendered management practices, this paper uses content analysis to examine corporate “emotional intelligence” (EI) and “emotional quotient” (EQ) training programs offered on platforms such as LinkedIn Learning, Udemy, and Skillsoft. Analyzing the socio-technical factors that enable historically feminized skills to become valued professional assets, I show how these platforms facilitate the “emotional androgenization of men and women” (Ilouz 2007, 37) while simultaneously flattening differences through a universalizing call for continual self-improvement. I argue that feminist theories of emotional labor offer critical new perspectives on technology and affect for scholars of computational media.

The Pleasures and Politics of Digital Skill in David Sudnow’s Pilgrim in the Microworld

Doug Stark, UNC Chapel Hill

This rereading of David Sudnow’s 1983 Pilgrim in the

Microworld departs from the text’s predominant treatment as a work of game studies *avant la lettre*. The article reframes Sudnow’s autoethnography as a perspective on the pleasures and politics of an important process in the history of technology: the cultural adoption of digital entertainment devices requiring skilled user interaction. Drawing on Peter Sloterdijk’s secular theory of asceticism, the article first unpacks how Sudnow’s Breakout (1978) training regime — informed by his piano background — furnishes an early account of the self-discipline required to cultivate the expert’s virtue of nonconscious, automatic play. Second, addressing Sudnow’s cyber-cultural allusions alongside his research into the economic logic of Breakout’s gameplay, the article contends that Pilgrim politicizes this virtuous automatism. Gaming skill, Sudnow reveals, is inextricable from a then emergent neuroeconomic assemblage. He thus complicates his earlier homology between piano training and video game training as paths to improvisational, egoless art, attesting to how the growing understanding of computers as expressive media assisted in their cultural legitimization. Finally, critiques acknowledged, the article concludes with a reparative reading of Sudnow’s ludic self-discipline as the cultivation of a pleasurable, ambivalent way of living with digital media that tacitly train us.

Language in computational media: an ethnographic approach

Gui Heurich, University College London

What is the role of language in computational media? Language tropes are frequently present in computational environments: programmers constantly work with the specific syntax of languages, compilers are built with linguistic models to translate source into machine code, algorithms are fraught with linguistic biases, natural language processing is a key aspect in contemporary graphical processing unit development, etc. And yet, language has not been used by many scholars as a primary device to think about and understand computational media. Based on ongoing ethnographic work with ruby programmers, this paper explores how programmers describe and conceptualize the role of language in the practice of computer programming. It builds on the notion of “language ideologies”, which is a concept developed in linguistic anthropology to refer to people’s implicit or explicit assumptions about the languages they are using and encountering in their everyday lives. As such, the paper focuses on the dominance of English as the computational lingua franca, and suggests that such dominance is not only relevant to understand programmers’ experiences of writing source code but also to discern the linguistic models currently used to develop compilers. In other words, a particular linguistic ideology - the grammar of American English - runs all the way through: from the hands of programmers to the core of machines. As such, the aim of this paper is to discuss the potential relevance of language as a transdisciplinary concept that highlights central aspects of computational media.

My Baby is a Computer: Notes on Nascent Computation

Rose Rowson, Brown University

In ‘My Mother was a Computer: Digital Subjects and Literary Texts’ (2005), N. Katherine Hayles proposes, via Friedrich Kittler’s ‘Discourse Networks 1800/1900’ (1985), that Mother Nature has been usurped by the Mother Computer as an explanatory model for the universe. Borrowed from Anne Balsamo (1996), the statement “my mother was a computer” straddles themes from the gendered clerical labor that undergirded mechanical computation in the early 20th century, to the internalization of computational processes by early 21st century digital subjects. This paper builds on the proposition made by Balsamo and Hayles by asking after generational descent. If my mother was a computer, then surely, I am a computer, too; if I am a mother computer, then would my also baby be a computer? Although metaphors of birth and babies have been applied to new technologies since at least the 19th century, I maintain here that the probabilistic tenets of

information theory that undergird computational processes complicate the causal model of direct lines of descent upon which birth metaphors rely. Indeed, Kittler's turn to information theory in his Afterword to 'Discourse Networks' as a means of subverting dominant hermeneutic modes of interpretation inaugurates a new problematic. We now know that information technologies cannot help us 'escape' subject positions, but how might these interpretive modes help us comprehend the metaphors used to describe information technologies? An introduction to a nascent line of enquiry, this presentation proposes a link between feminist science studies, (computational) media theory and metahistorical interpretation.

Session Organizers:

Ranjodh Singh Dhaliwal, University of Notre Dame
Théo Lepage-Richer, Brown University

Chair:

Annika Butler-Wall

079. Climate Data Relations

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

In these times of shifting climate relations, we find technoscience regimes bound up in assemblages of data produced with predictive models; data that shape the agendas of international political convenings; data about topics as disparate as temperature, displacement, and armed conflict; data that deal in narratives about the future while vying to mediate relations in the present. How do we responsibly make sense of predictive climate models, their data, their code, and their attendant relations of power? How much do we make sense overall of ecologically inflected data regimes? How might we responsibly unpack these data and models while intervening in processes through which they uphold and reproduce systemic forms of oppression? Dare we envision better or even good climate data relations? The first session of the Climate Data Relations panel is entitled "Data and the Environment."

Participants:

The Datapoint Plant and the Misplaced Bee: Shifting Materialities in Environmental Sciences Data Practices.

Felipe Mammoli, Unicamp - University of Campinas

This work explores some ways in which the environmental sciences apprehend the environment as data. I present two ethnographic encounters: 1) with a climate model developed in Brazil to produce predictions about the effects of climate change in the Amazon Forest, and how a plant is understood as a series of intersecting datapoints to be processed by algorithms inside of this model; and 2) with a bee that was found without any catalog information in the Hymenoptera (ant, bees and wasp) Collection in the Museum of Natural History - Berlin, and it's now used to calibrate a mass digitisation device responsible to digitize the 2.8 million objects in the collection. The decomposed plant is untraceable back to its origin due to the successive processes of data cleaning, harmonization and transformations it has to endure to be able to work alongside the informational infrastructure of global climate change sciences. The misplaced bee is unidentifiable both historically and taxonomically since there is no metadata about when, where or who have collected it, challenging its status as a natural history object. By contrasting the two, I show how the plant and the bee are reconfigured as they flow from one informational system to the next, disconnecting data collection from colonial past and transforming databasing practices into the future of global biodiversity. Datafication threatens to sanitize the environment as uncontested and universal, but a close attention to its practices reveals moments where materiality leaks, creating space for meaningful interactions.

The Post-Environmental Condition? *Antonia Walford, University College London*

Inspired by Jenny Reardon's diagnosis of the 'post-genomic condition' - where, in the face of massive amounts of genomic

data being produced, genomicists confront the problem of what the data actually means, and for who - this paper enquires about what might be called the 'post-environmental condition'. The environment as a social, historical and political space is increasingly becoming datafied: modelling data, military remote sensing data, terrestrial and maritime sensor data, local environmental monitoring systems, citizen science data projects, are being 'joined up' through international databasing initiatives that claim to go beyond territorial and epistemological borders; Big Tech promises "AI for Earth" and the "Planetary Computer", framing the earth as one global data and AI network; government environmental databases have been the stage for dramatic political protest. However, for the most part, the questions of what this environmental data is, what it means, and for who, remain critically unexamined. Although those working in environmental justice have brought attention to the way in which land has been appropriated or polluted, natural resources exhausted and stolen, and people dispossessed of their environmental security in ways that re-inscribe colonial racist logics, relatively little attention has been paid to environmental data itself as a key site of power. Starting at the scale of spectacular planetary data imaginaries, this paper begins to map out the mechanisms of these apparently new digital territories of environmental governance, and their social and political implications, by paying ethnographic attention to their relational dynamics and mundane technological processes that underpin them.

Checkpoints, Tipping Points and Points of No Return - Programming Environmental Stewardship into Gamespace
Edmund Konroyd-Bolden, York U

Videogames and their productive capacities are well suited for various articulations from STS. Videogames not only relay representations of the world, they allow for continual, iterative authorship, community and even, hacking of worlds - real and virtual. They are thus productive spaces for testing theories and making arguments about STS themes such as the body, visibility, or the systems of the world (e.g. ecological or economic ones). The latter is the focus of this paper. Some troubling habits of natural resource game mechanics (i.e. confluence of goals, affordances, rules/limits, etc.) also happen to reflect the real world and its regimes of political-environmental time that govern climate change. These habits are subverted through a new videogame mechanic where harvest and consequent physical, environmental impacts are subject to an accelerated decision-making structure. Governing simulation of time in this manner brings immediacy to issues of hyper-extractive strategy and ensures proper consequence recognition/association. The arguments about economic efficiency and the representative power of local impacts are informed by a foundation of Elinor Ostrom's economics, and intersectional practice like that of Stephen Sheppard, respectively. The ideas and simulation are executed according to standards of provocative video game practice and align with Abraham's theoretical work about climate futures. The procedural rhetoric offered by the game is one of resource intelligence that is inherently good and actionable, though far from rigidly imposed. The need for reciprocal relations toward a stable environmental future is made clear through the acceleration of time and physics mediated by the game-engine.

The incorporation of SDGs by the Brazilian scientific community: a case study of scientific productions developed at Unicamp and USP *Thais Aparecida Dibbern, University of Campinas (Unicamp); Milena Serafim, University of Campinas (Unicamp)*

This article aims to analyze how the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) can be incorporated by the scientific community, specifically in relation to the social commitment to be assumed by public universities. Furthermore, we will map, in terms of

scientific publications, what has been produced at the University of Campinas (Unicamp) and the University of São Paulo (USP) on the topic of the SDGs, during the period of January 2016 to January 2021 (5 years). Methodologically, this article will be based on bibliographic review and scientific articles about the SDGs theme, as well as through access to public databases such as Scielo, Web of Science, Scopus, Capes Publications Portal, Brazilian Digital Library of Theses and Dissertations (BDTD), Repository of Scientific and Intellectual Production of Unicamp and Digital Library of Intellectual Production of USP. As selected keywords, “Sustainable Development Goals”, “2030 Agenda” and “Post-2015 Agenda”, will be considered in English, Portuguese and Spanish. Therefore, this article hopes to contribute to the recent debates about the relationship between the scientific community and the SDGs.

Session Organizer:

S. Hayley Steele, University of California at Davis

Chair:

S. Hayley Steele, University of California at Davis

080. Bernal Prize celebration: On whose shoulders we stand.

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

In this session the two Bernal Prize winners of this year will give their presentations. Although awards are important in acknowledging the relevance of specific contributions to our field, it is equally important to go beyond the idea of considering scholarly outputs as achievements of individuals. In the session we therefore adopt the feminist politics of remembering on whose shoulders we stand. After the two talks of the Bernal prize winners the participants are invited to tell about which scholars/ideas/publications have been most inspiring in their work.

Session Organizers:

Judy Wajcman, LSE

Nelly Oudshoorn, University of Twente

Chair:

Sally Wyatt, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Maastricht Univer

081. Building Better Worlds, Brick by Plastic Brick

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

“Rebuild the world,” The LEGO Group’s (TLG) recent marketing campaign, encourages us to view our world through a child’s eyes: to see “opportunities” where adults typically see “challenges.” The slogan seems to click with the SSSS conference theme of addressing “unequal and uncertain worlds” though the fit is not that snug: in LEGO’s campaign, there is no mention of matters that ought to prompt collective “rebuilding,” such as ecological catastrophe, the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic, and the rise of ethno-nationalism. Nonetheless, the slogan aptly describes LEGO’s own increasing ubiquity; a “killer app” for stay-at-home orders and virtual schooling, LEGO products are selling out often before they are made, even as TLG opens new production plants around the world and aggressively litigates against knock-off blocks in its efforts to fill our own worlds with its palpable plastic pixels. Clearly, LEGO itself is engaged in a very concerted project to rebuild our world. What are the material-discursive practices that constitute this rebuilding? To address this question, our panel builds on the platform provided by LEGOfied: Building Blocks as Media. This edited volume draws extensively from STS to consider LEGO as a “materially digital” medium, a pleasurable tactile and infinitely malleable enactment of digital logics through which almost anything can be refashioned using its atomistic and recombinatory elements, or “LEGOfied.” Each panelist extends this concept to examine specific environmental, economic, epistemic, and aesthetic dimensions of LEGO’s “world (re)building,” while collectively demonstrating how STS is uniquely equipped to reckon with these sites of ambivalent construction.

Participants:

LEGOfied Science **Kate Maddalena**, University of Toronto

The LEGO brand, particularly in its millennial and more open-source-friendly renaissance, has always allied itself with the ethos of the technoscientific endeavour. One of the very first packages you might call a “set,” for example, was a moon rocket that came out in the same year that the US entered the space race. In the turbulent years of 2020-2021, LEGO and many of its fan communities have doubled down on the commitment to pro-technoscience rhetoric and have continued to manifest a largely utopic attitude towards technology’s potential to “rebuild [a] world” that daily seems badly in need of an update. As early as April 2020 on a user-produced Youtube channel, a minifig Justin Trudeau memed the Canadian prime minister and joined the voices teaching us what “social distancing” meant. Meanwhile, LEGO marketing launched the “Build the Change” campaign, asking kids to use LEGO to imagine the planet’s environmental future. This talk will examine multiple sites of LEGO users’ and the LEGO brand’s contributions to LEGO’s always-emergent ethos that respond to the SARS-CoV2 and climate crises in order to ask: what does the LEGO community seem to think “rebuilding” really means?

LEGOfied Platforms *Nicholas Taylor*

Understanding LEGO as a platform seems straightforward: metaphors of construction, connection, and support abound, particularly in LEGO’s promotional materials. This presentation considers TLG’s recent forays into platformization: techniques by which it can both distribute and more tightly regulate its materially and immaterially digital property. Specifically, it considers TLG’s 2019 acquisition of Bricklink, a fan-run marketplace for buying and selling second-hand LEGO as well as user-created building instructions. For its substantial user base, Bricklink operates as an infrastructure for the circulation of aftermarket LEGO products and LEGO-related labor, a vital extension of the infrastructure TLG already has in place for distributing LEGO from factories to stores. A material-discursive re-alignment of Bricklink soon followed this acquisition, as TLG halted circulation of knock-off blocks and modified LEGO, as well as building instructions featuring intellectual property not currently licensed to TLG. Bricklink now carries out, at the level of infrastructure, the boundary work of sorting LEGO from not-LEGO that TLG has been engaged in across multiple other domains, often with the enthusiastic involvement of LEGO enthusiasts: legal (suing makers of LEGO-compatible bricks); ideological (positioning LEGO as ‘the’ building block); and material (removing impure debris and other toys from LEGO collections). Given these efforts, it is no longer sufficient to define LEGO’s world-building ambitions primarily in terms of its “transmedia” aspirations across representational media. Rather, LEGO increasingly resembles other “infrastructuralized platforms” such as Steam or Facebook: an apparatus for connection and content creation, certainly, but one whose channels are more tightly governed than they appear.

LEGOfied Sound *Malcolm Ogden, NC State University*

In early 2021, TLG released an official album on Spotify, entitled “LEGO White Noise.” Each of the seven 30-minute tracks on the album features a unique, distinctively textured encounter with LEGO blocks, as indicated by track titles like “Searching for the One (Brick)” and “The Waterfall.” TLG’s aesthetic repurposing of the sounds of LEGO blocks for unobtrusive ambient accompaniment to other mundane activities can be situated in relation to a host of other kinds of mostly longform ambient media which have proliferated online in recent years, such as ambient, white noise, and ASMR videos on YouTube, LoFi hip-hop streams, and meditation/relaxation apps such as the Calm app. In this paper, I argue that, particularly in light of the abundance of already-existing unofficial LEGO ASMR and white noise content on the YouTube platform, the “LEGO White Noise” album serves as a clear demonstration of how TLG has attempted to capitalize off of the “pleasurably tactile and infinitely malleable” nature of LEGO blocks — in this

case, by situating the unique sonic affordances of LEGO blocks alongside a host of other quasi-therapeutic digital ambient/atmospheric media. Here, the platformized production of LEGO, and associated processes of “world (re)building,” involve not only representational and tactical media, but sonic media as well.

Plantified LEGO *Chris Ingraham, University of Utah*

There are 915,103,765 different ways to combine six identical eight-stud LEGO bricks. Add just one more, let alone others of different shapes and sizes, and the possibilities grow exponentially. From the standpoint of sheer structural possibility, LEGO truly is a worldbuilding technology. But if the possible configurations of LEGOified “worlds” approaches the infinite, that’s because of the LEGO brick’s constitutive modularity. These bricks can be added to one another in such a way that the removal of some does not necessarily lead to the destruction of the whole. Of course, LEGO is neither the first modular technology utilized by humans for the purposes of (re)building worlds, nor is modularity itself a human invention. For that, we turn to the plant kingdom, our planet’s only modular living beings. Humans have essential organs in discrete places; remove one and the rest of our bodies fail. But plants have their essential features distributed throughout the organism; if they lose a branch, a stem, a leaf, they still survive. This paper explores what the relation between plant modularity and the modularity of worldbuilding technologies like LEGO can teach us about the relationship between nature and culture, a false binary better characterized as “natures-cultures” (Latour) or “natureculture” (Haraway). By considering the case of the famous Crystal Palace, first constructed for the Great Exhibition of 1851 in London (and inspired explicitly by the modularity of plants), I ultimately show how the modularity of plants makes them the original builders and rebuilders of worlds.

Session Organizer:

Nicholas Taylor

082. Technologies for claiming our kin - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

The infrastructure and practices for administering colonization, slavery, and capitalist heritable property relations are the basis for proliferating genealogical technologies, from DNA databases to family tree websites. These technologies materially and socially support white settler genealogical practices that identify away from responsibilities for the material conditions and effects of whiteness, and towards race shifting and the appropriation of racialized identities. However, increasingly people are also developing projects for claiming kin that do not erase the histories and ongoing practices of land theft, genocide, enslavement, and border militarism. The two sessions for “Technologies for claiming our kin” investigate data, stories, material practices, and dreaming that allow people to claim kin other than the typical history of genealogy. What are the forms of relationality through which people might “claim bad kin,” or collect their relations when their relations are the agents of tremendous harm? What practices of claiming kin resist the social organization of forgetting of histories, familial and otherwise, that fall outside the settler state’s conception of being related? How do we build relationality in new kin formations, and what social and technical practices support such work? These sessions address human and non-human, microbial and chemical, technical and social infrastructures of relationality.

Participants:

A sustainable genealogy of pine and pesticides *Evan Hepler-Smith, Duke University*

This paper argues for a genealogical, relational conception of what chemicals are, what they do, and how they might be and do better. It does so based on historical research-in-progress on pine forestry in the US South—historically tied to antebellum tar and turpentine production, promoted as a promising source of renewable energy and sustainable chemical feedstocks, and

implicated in ongoing processes of environmental racism—focusing on the global history of one pine forestry product, the chlorinated pine-resin “toxaphene,” the world’s most extensively used pesticide by weight circa the 1970s. Slavery, ecological havoc, illness, death, boom-and-bust cycles of cotton agriculture and pesticide resistance in Egypt, toxification of human-water-fish lifeways in the Great Lakes—these are some relations we can trace. One might sum costs against countervailing benefits, submitting sustainability to a balance sheet. That is one way to reckon with relations. There are others, as, for example, Robin Wall Kimmerer relates in an essay on pine forests, products, and relations. This paper works toward an equivocal, ongoing, genealogical conception of toxaphene and its chemical families (so to speak). Analytically, this paper takes up Michelle Murphy’s call for reckoning with chemicals as “complex bundles of extensive relations,” Gabrielle Hecht’s concept of “interscalar vehicles” (objects and methods of practice traversing spatiotemporal scales), and Lissa Roberts’ and Simon Werrett’s approach to telling “compound histories” of chemical substances, building on but looking beyond my own studies of the world-making paperwork of “molecular bureaucracy.”

Fermenting American Spirituality: Theorizing Microbial-Human Relation by Nourishing the Gut-Brain Terrain *Alison Renna, Yale University*

Since 2004, microbiome-gut-brain axis science has built a swelling argument that the fermenting populations of bacteria, archaea, and fungi in the human gut have some role to play in processes of human cognition. As scientists and philosophers debate different models to map the boundaries between the human body and the life processes of microbes in its mucous membranes (as a holobiont, a metaorganism, an ecology, an assemblage?) a quick skim through any grocery store aisle or health magazine will show that American “wellness” culture has enthusiastically taken up the proposition that to modify the microbiome is to modify the mood and mind, and has begun to offer its own theories which include the vocabularies and concerns of American spirituality. As historian of American metaphysical religion Catherine Albanese teaches us, to theorize the mind in these spiritual flows of American culture is always to build on the lineage of a panoply of America’s intertwined spiritual and scientific histories. [Albanese 2009] This lineage’s production of metaphors of connectivity is no better exemplified than at the Kripalu Yoga Retreat center’s May 2019 seminar on “nourishing the gut-brain terrain.” At this seminar, participants (including psychologists, counselors, dieticians, and spiritual seekers of all kinds) were promised that proper cultivation of gut bacteria (in processes that combined scientific nutrition, microbial supplementation, and meditation on human connectivity with the earth through its biomes) would create an enhanced spiritual connection with the natural world via the conduit of the fermentation of microbes in their mucous membranes. While the seminar carried the authority of scientific education and offered continuing education credits to the dieticians and psychologists in attendance, the seminar’s conveners were also actively interested in interpreting bodily fermentation as a site through which they might subvert the restrictive models of connectivity which were available in mainstream scientific medicine. By showing how the complexity and ambiguity of a body’s microbial state—always tethered to particularities of geography, human experience, and global ecology—they argued that the study and modification of the body could never be subject simply to the maps science provides, but rather was made up by living connections between species and worlds. The seminar participants became theorists who argued that to understand microbial-human connectivity was to re-theorize the entire project of scientific medicine. I argue that the maps participants re-drew to understand the body combined then-leading scientific theories in gut-brain-axis science with the lineages of metaphysical religion in the USA—universalistic and

pluralistic spiritual vocabularies of ancient wisdom, indigenous knowledge, feminist practice, and human care--to create a new map of microbial-human connection. This paper draws from ethnographic work by the author at this seminar and oral history interviews with the scientists who developed key research upon which the seminar was formed to historicize the main scientific and spiritual ingredients conveners combined as they smoothed over the inadequacies of scientific medicine with the concerns of feminist spiritual culture. Fermentation became a site through which the seminar's conveners and participants re-imagined their relationship with the world, and their theories of fermentation help us consider the stakes and ingredients of the maps we draw from the ambiguity of fermentation when we build our own metaphors. This essay adds to the work of feminist STS scholars like Haraway and Tsing to argue that we must account for the complexity of spiritual theories of interspecies connectivity, especially as they blossom out of science itself--or we will miss the work of science in society as it acts in American culture today.

Resisting False Relationality: Reification, Generalization and Decontextualization as Barriers to Kin Connection Through Databases *Nikki Stevens, Arizona State University*

Modern relational database technologies, despite their name, do not facilitate the project of making and maintaining good relations. In fact, several of the specific techniques of relational database creation and modeling reinforce white supremacist and cisgender-normative approaches to connection. While STS examines its preoccupation with whiteness (Mascarenhas 2018), and critical data studies notes the (white-cis) bias in datasets, there is a lack of specific, applied technical information on how these biases are introduced at the level of the data model. This project reviews three specific technical moves that relational database designers employ that mirror the techniques of white-cisness: reification, generalization and decontextualization. I then offer a process of data modeling that subverts these processes and counters white-cis notions of teleological and linear time, providing ways to connect to relations across time and space. Finally, I argue that efforts to reclaim kin and to envision new relations must move past the white-cis technological frameworks and limitations. In order to do that, we must first identify them, and then envision new ways to connect through and around data-centric infrastructures. By resisting white-cis data modeling techniques and the teleological push of white-cis time, we can nurture tools that provide expansive ways to (re)connect.

Session Organizer:

Scout Calvert

Discussant:

Alexis Shotwell, Carleton University

083. Rethinking Outer Space And Science: Critical Engagements With The Cosmos And The Extra-terrestrial - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

A Cosmological Chiasmus- Searches for Extraterrestrial Life, 1950-Present *Claire Isabel Webb, University of Southern California*

Scientists who search for life beyond Earth—either “weird” life forms (Helmreich, 2009), or extraterrestrial intelligence (Webb 2020)—pursue objects that are not extant and are as yet unperceived. As such, these scientists often fall back on rhetorical strategies to imagine, relate to, and build experimental assemblages toward alien beings or microbial life. Inspired by Lisa Messeri’s “gestures of cosmic relation” (2017) as a way to theorize how astronomers use their bodies to form imaginations of other worlds (e.g., pointing to an extrasolar planet), this paper inquires after scientists who deploy literary devices to shape possibilities of other forms of life. I explore one such instances,

which I call a cosmological chiasmus. From the Greek, a chiasma (χίασμα) is an “arrangement of two lines (sticks, etc.) crossed like the letter X” (OED), and in literature a chiasmus is “a grammatical figure by which the order of words in one of two parallel clauses is inverted in the other” (OED). This paper theorizes how, since the Space Age, scientists’ fears and hopes have animated the planetary and the extraplanetary, forming a four-point figure: a cosmological chiasmus. Using historical NASA documents and drawing on over four years of fieldwork with SETI researchers, I will explore how, from the postwar to the post-world, fears of terrestrial apocalypse have animated projects to find or even become extraterrestrials. This paper will consider the concept of being indigenous to, and extraterrestrial from, Earth through decolonial scholarship.

Reframing ‘Space: the Final Frontier’ *Lauren Reid, Freie Universität*

“Space: the final frontier,” declared William Shatner-as-Captain Kirk in Star Trek’s 1966 opening sequence. From the early days of human space exploration to today, concepts of outer space and the frontier have been entangled in popular public imaginaries, particularly in the United States where the myths of the frontier layers together imagery of the cosmos with colonial imagery of U.S. America’s 19th century ‘Wild West’. The ‘frontier’ solidifies a colonial approach to space as an environment to mine for resources, to cultivate (aka terraform) and to domestically inhabit. In what ways can we think beyond, hegemonic and time-worn cosmic narratives led by dominant space-focused communities? How might we shake off the historic spectre of the U.S. American frontier that so limits imaginaries and practices of space exploration? This paper takes a lateral approach to these questions by focusing on the ‘frontier’ of ‘space: the final frontier’ and the word’s many different meanings across times and geographies. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork with space-related communities in Thailand, this paper hones in on two Thai historic notions of the frontier: the animist jungle that is alive with spirits and political territories that are delineated by wild zones rather than hard borders. Through this reframing exercise, I aim to open up a speculative space to de-centre, localise and pluralise knowledge production in the field of space science.

Planetary Protection and the Icy Moons of Jupiter and Saturn *Laura Lilla Farkas, Science and Technology Studies, York University*

The icy moons of Jupiter and Saturn are of major relevance to the question of habitability within our solar system. As they are thought to harbour subsurface oceans, they are among the most important subjects of astrobiological research in its search for life beyond Earth. Since these worlds are now serve as some of the primary targets for future exploratory missions, the planetary protection policies that serve to guide these undertakings are increasingly coming into focus as well. The aim of this paper is to look at the ways in which these environments, the relevant planetary protection policies, and the modes of remote robotic exploration are being conceptualized. In addition, it intends to situate these within particular imaginings and narratives that include the concepts of colonial expansion, technoliberalism, and Euro-American racial capitalism, while it also seeks to gauge how they might maintain or reproduce these lifeworlds. In addition to the relevant literature, the present paper identifies a few key points and concerns based on a set of interviews conducted with experts in planetary protection related fields. It is widely anticipated that due to the rapidly growing scientific and corresponding private interests, within the next decade or so the exploration of these icy moons will enter its next phase. As this will lead us to uncharted waters both out there and here on Earth, it is important to look at these present developments as their performative effects could have far reaching consequences in more than one sense of the word.

Lithosociality in and in relation to outer space *Julie Michelle*

Klinger, University of Delaware

This paper introduces lithosociality as a framework for conceptualizing the social relations embedded in mineral worlds in the context of human engagements with outer space. It consists of four pillars: (1) Critical geographies of mineral supply chains and capital flows for space-linked infrastructure and space technologies; (2) Metabolic processes across the biotic and abiotic matter on and beyond Earth; (3) Cultural practices of investigation, sense- and value-making, and; (4) Forms of social (dis)organization that create, constrain, or erase modes of relation across the mineral – technosocial – biological domains. The purpose is to posit a way of thinking across mineral processes, resource use, and space sciences that contextualizes—rather than simply being coterminous with—colonial extractive ambitions.

“The restaurant at the end of the world” *Aaron Parkhurst, UCL; 2018 Jeevendrampillai, UCL Anthropology/City, University of London*

Since the first seeds of wheat, pea, maize and onion were taken into space aboard sputnik 4 in 1960, there have been numerous experiments on plants in space to explore photosynthesis and plant growth under different conditions. More recently, there are many life science and botanical research projects aboard the international space station in which astronauts cultivate plants for consumption, asking questions on the feasibility and sustainability of ‘gardening’ off world. The gardening systems on the ISS, such as the vegetable production system (VEGGIE) and the Advanced Plant Habitat (APH), have been successful in cultivating a range of edible plants, including forms of lettuce, radishes and mustard greens. The narratives that accompany these experiments, from astronaut researchers on the ISS, space agency media feeds, and the life-science researchers and laboratories on Earth that partner with the ISS, are marked by optimism for the ‘future of humanity’, the hope and hype of expanding human civilization off-world, the positive effects of greenery and growing plants for psychological well-being, and increasingly, the immediate concerns of sustainable sources of nutrients for the Artemis missions to the moon, and beyond to Mars. This chapter explores such narratives on the role of plants in space, and the meaning that people derive from these plants as representative forms of life and utopic desires. However, in doing so, this chapter challenges such narratives and explores a more subtle, yet equally powerful sentiment of ruin and eschatology. We argue that plants and gardening on the ISS, as mediators of future making, are objects and practices marked by irony and contradiction, characterized by contesting claims of utopia and eschatology. Borrowing from anthropological and material culture analytics on utopia, science, and the Anthropocene, the chapter extends beyond the context of outer-space to ask: as the Earth heats and ecological catastrophe abounds, what are the emergent forms of plant/human relations in the end of times, and what is being consumed at the restaurant at the end of the world?

Session Organizers:

Eleanor Armstrong, University of Delaware

Julie Michelle Klinger, University of Delaware

084. The algorithmic turn of prediction - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Throughout history, the future has been an important reference for mankind. Its role for life in the present, however, has changed significantly in the course of time. While the future was initially found to be unalterable, with the development of modern societies it became to be understood as an open horizon that stands in a causal relationship to the present – the future got shapable according to actions and decisions in the present. This shift in terms of interpreting the future made it even more attractive than before to produce knowledge about it. Predictive strategies subsequently flourished and technologies thereby played an increasingly important role. With the advent of modern forms of algorithmic data analysis, with machine

learning and artificial intelligence gaining center stage, another shift in referring to the future is likely, presenting an exciting as well as urgent challenge for social sciences in general and STS in particular. Before this backdrop, this panel aims to discuss the theoretical as well as empirical implications of algorithmic prediction in the datafied society. What effects does the algorithmization of prediction have on the systems, settings and situations concerned? How do algorithmic predictive technologies differ from their – allegedly less sophisticated – technological predecessors? And, last but not least, where are the analytical possibilities and limits of STS approaches regarding the algorithmic turn of prediction?

Participants:

Before the Disaster Strikes *Michael Nagenborg, University of Twente; Yola Georgiadou, University of Twente; Marc van den Homberg, 510; Caroline Gevaert, University of Twente*

In our explorative paper, we want to outline the challenges of using predictive algorithms to provide humanitarian aid. We consider the 510's Impact Based Forecasting (<https://www.510.global/impact-based-forecast/>) as an early example in the humanitarian space before act before a disaster happens. We will use our work on hyper-proactive techno-security (Nagenborg & Weber, 2020) as a starting point to get a better understanding of the unique challenges of anticipatory actions in the humanitarian context. On the one hand, we will compare predictive policing as a relatively well-studied application domain for predictive algorithms. On the other hand, we will look into the role of forecasting, planning, and anticipation in organizing humanitarian response and capacity building. Here, we will primarily focus on the role of prediction in increasing disaster resilience. The second line of inquiry is vital for avoiding the wrong assumption that prediction didn't play any role in organizing and delivering humanitarian aid. Yet, we would like to argue that predictive aid leads to a blurring of the boundary between "disaster response" and "disaster preparedness." By participating in this open panel, we would like to get a better grip of the particularities of using predictive algorithms in humanitarian aid while offering insights into the specific temporal dynamics of disaster response.

Negotiating Urban Representation for Digital Urban Twins
Johanna Fleischer

In this talk, I will present my initial field experience in building a new system for urban prediction making. In order to plan modern cities, it has always been obligatory to archive and evaluate a wealth of data. These processes were resource-intensive and required a lot of time and labor to link the plethora of information stored in data silos and analog archives. As the digitization of urban information for planning continues, we are seeing a dramatic change in this practice. Not only is collecting and recording different, especially through information and communication systems, but the ability to link data through algorithms and machine-driven analysis is radically changing practice. Therefore, municipal management bodies in many cities have started to develop new ideas for analysis and communication. One prominent achievement is the concept of Digital Urban Twins (DUT). The DUT is an abstract digitized model of the city. It is connected to the environment to collect and visualize real-time data, mainly for urban planning, environmental impact simulation and socio-economic research for predictive models of the future. My research focuses on the construction of such a system in the cities of Munich, Leipzig, Hamburg and Helsinki. For this purpose, I resort to a classical form of STS research design to observe the discourse between agents in the construction process. The goal is to reveal the relevant parameters that are built into the predictive system. What I want to find out in my research is how it is negotiated which parameters are considered representative for predictive systems.

The Logic Of Post-diction And The Predictive Paradigm Of Machine Learning *Paola Lopez, University of Vienna;*

Florian Eyert, Weizenbaum Institute for the Networked Society

With the increasing production, processing and analysis of data, attempts to predict future developments have largely turned to the calculation of probabilities through algorithmic systems. Examples are the prediction of job performance in automated hiring, of recidivism in criminal justice, and of need in the allocation of welfare resources. With machine learning, data-driven algorithmic systems have become the tools of choice. The current rhetoric of efficiency and objectivity through mathematical sophistication is, however, accompanied by growing academic and activist concerns regarding risks such as biased datafications and resulting unfair decisions. In this talk we argue that, contrary to current attempts to fix such problems with technical means, these problems are rather inherent in the epistemic foundation of prediction via machine learning itself. We characterize the general outline of this data-driven predictive paradigm and argue that algorithmic predictions would more aptly be described as “post-dictions”, that generalize from past and supra-individual patterns to future individual behaviour in an epistemically highly fragile manner. Taking into account this epistemic foundation can inform a more rigorous academic and public debate about the fairness of machine-learning-based predictions. By means of three brief case studies we illustrate possible avenues of such a debate going forward: reversing the temporal logic of prediction tools in order to detect inequalities, using the notion of recourse in order to improve institutional dynamics rather than blame individuals and, lastly, considering more seriously the preconditions for deploying machine-learning-based prediction at all.

Session Organizers:

Maximilian Heimstädt, Bielefeld University

Elena Esposito, Bielefeld University

Chair:

Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld

085. Un/Making a Difference 2: design, environment, more-than-human entanglements & refusals

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Resistance through Un/Making *kristina lindström*, *Malmö University*; *Åsa Ståhl*, *Department of Design, Linnaeus University*

In this paper we will discuss our work in the Un/Making Studio that was set up to explore the practice of un/making, recognising both construction and destruction in all kinds of making (Fry 2009, Tonkinwise 2019). Whereas most design sets out to make change through the making of new things, we have explored mundane practices of unmaking, in order to make space for alternatives (Feola 2019). The studio has engaged with already ongoing, emerging, anticipated, intentional or unintentional processes of unmaking such as banning the plastic straw, cleaning of polluted soil in previous industrial design areas and loss of biodiversity. Our design interventions have approached these large scale unmakings with, what can seem as, mundane acts and actions for example by picking plastic waste, stop using single use plastic items, planting seeds in polluted soil and cooking food with an awareness of how the fruits and berries were pollinated. However, we argue that taken together these design interventions make space for relationships that prefigure radical change since they resist tendencies within design and beyond to privilege the new, progress and thin futures.

Tending Sheep, Making Good Relations *Anne Galloway*, *Victoria University of Wellington*

For more than a decade I have studied New Zealand sheep farming. Although the size of the national flock has decreased

significantly since its height in the 1980s, the extensive farming of vast numbers of sheep for wool, milk, and meat remains common practice and an economic mainstay for our small, isolated island nation during uncertain times. Imperatives of efficiency and productivity drive the industry, and rely on complex global technoscientific webs of artificial insemination, embryo transfer, scanning, pharmaceutical, feed supplement, and mass processing techniques. This paper offers an autoethnographic account of tending a small flock of rare-breed sheep in ways that fail to meet local definitions of “real farming”. But it is precisely this failure that I seek to reposition as a mundane form of resistance to the industrial logic of mass livestock production and consumption. From my choice of breed to naming each animal and killing them myself to feed my family, I tend our flock in ways that challenge the presumed inherent killability of sheep, interrogate unequal power relations between human and nonhuman animals, and offer glimpses of how to live in good relation with companions I may eventually eat. Ultimately, I present our shared lives as a way to practice everyday, radical politics and ethics, and I invite others to consider the possibility that the world is already otherwise.

Un/Making a Difference: Interspecies Knowledge-Making through Clothing Inventions *Katja May*, *Goldsmiths, University of London*

This paper explores how clothing inventions mediate interspecies relationship. Using in-depth visual and document analysis, this paper looks at 200 years of clothing patents that connect humans and animals in the European patent archive in the Politics of Patents project. Patents are an insightful source for studying “world making” practices as they feature often small or unassuming alterations or novelties to existing types of clothing, thus documenting extra-ordinary acts of mundane resistance. “Clothing is a socio-technical device that enables, constrains and organises bodies in different ways” (Jungnickel, 2020). This paper examines how inventors have utilised clothing in ways to outline, define, perforate or erase the boundaries of the human body in relation to the nonhuman with visions of interspecies intimacy, care and companionship clearly driving inventors’ creations from the 1980s onwards. As humans carry cats around in sweaters, pet birds accompany people on special shoulder perches and dogs receive spa treatments with massage gloves, touch - and in particular the kind of touch mediated (enabled, restricted or reinforced) through a garment- emerges as a key element to shaping multispecies relationships. To touch the animal is to be in touch with the animal, and to enter into its perception of the world. Clothing patents, thus, are speculative models of interspecies knowledge-making that envision and enable new forms interspecies encounter and togetherness and decentering the human in debates about citizenship.

The way young mycelia do: a fungal approach towards ruined worlds *Vitor França Netto Chiodi*, *University of Campinas*

In my PhD research I work with fungal companions in order to speculate what could be mycelial thinking and writing and how to use them to think about the end of the world. Inspired by their radial world-making, the challenge is taking the ruined worlds into account on shorter scales, within the reach of our tentacles, like young mycelia do. Young fungal colonies show a very peculiar behavior, where they explore their surroundings by growing radially, like an expanding ring, learning about the place they live. Then, the colony deliberates which partnerships they are building next in an assembly already affected by the surroundings. At last, they create relations with living and non-living partners that change the initial circle, producing something new and unpredictable. These three steps might suggest a methodology to reform the way we deal with ruined places. Changing the ecosystems, mycelia create possibilities for some forms of life to emerge and others to disappear. New ecologies are always made by many. What mycelia do that deserve a central place in this narrative is that they create possibilities for

life in places that seem to be doomed. And that is why they are a good image to think-with on the end of the world, with what Donna Haraway called "neither hope, nor despair". This art-science essay attempts to make sense out of the mutual impact between the studying of fungi and contemporary feminist STS, leading to an approach where ontology, ethics and epistemology are inseparable from one another.

Technology of the Oppressed: Inequity and the digital mundane in Favelas of Brazil *David Nemer, University of Virginia*

Given the understanding that digital technology can mask and deepen oppression, the question becomes: how can the oppressed use digital technologies in their quest to liberate themselves and regain their humanity? To address this question, I animate stories of humans living in the favelas of Brazil who creatively and critically appropriate technologies in their journey to find liberation- I called this Mundane Technology. Mundane Technology is not a term that I coined- it has actually been explored by previous STS scholars interested in understanding the role of technology in our everyday life. While I borrow the notion of everyday life technologies, I expand the term Mundane Technology to go beyond digital artifacts. Rather, they refer to processes of the oppressed appropriating everyday technologies—technological artifacts, operations, and spaces—and using them to alleviate oppression in their everyday lives. Mundane Technology also encompasses “non-productive” activities and desires that people engage with through quotidian digital technologies. Mundane Technology is a decolonial framework aimed at understanding how people exercise their agency and, in Paulo Freire’s terms, consciousness and appropriate technologies to mobilize themselves toward a quality of life they desire. Thus, Mundane Technology is how technology is reinterpreted, adapted, and reinvented by those outside the centers of power in order to achieve liberation from oppression. Approaching Mundane Technology as appropriations of technology opens new research avenues for culture and technology, and contributes to a renewed concern with democracy. This talk is based on my book “Technology of the Oppressed” (forthcoming 2022, MIT Press).

Session Organizer:

Kat Jungnickel, Goldsmiths, University of London

Chair:

Laura Forlano, Illinois Institute of Technology

086. Relations and Troubles of Tools of Valuation – III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

Sorting cells out: an inquiry into the circulation and valuation of cord blood units *Pierre Delvenne, Université de Liège (SPIRAL)*; *Hadrien Macq, Technische Universität München*; *Céline Parotte, University of Liege - Spiral*

Novel entities like stem-cells and related medical therapies not only encapsulate huge hopes for medical treatments, they have also become key sites of capital accumulation. The valuation of life science objects has been treated in several ways in recent years. In STS, a first strand addresses the value of tissues and body parts mainly in terms of commodification. By contrast, a second strand emphasizes the importance of assetization as the key driver in technoscientific capitalism. Finally, anthropological contributions interested in valuation often question the boundary between commodity and gift. In this paper, we take stock of these contributions by empirically studying the donation of cord blood units (CBUs) and following their multiple paths (i.e. release for storage, direct use, trash) as co-modified with infrastructures that translate and valorize them. We develop a framework to address the set of practices and operations that constitute and configure multiple, potentially conflicting, forms of ‘value’ (i.e. economic, political, therapeutic, scientific). Relying on prolonged

ethnographic research conducted in a cell therapy laboratory of a university hospital in Belgium, we find that the performance of sorting cells out is a crucial tool of valuation, as it dramatically affects the circulation, value and status of cells. By providing compelling evidence that moving cells to the market thrives on the interplay between strategies of turning living entities into gifts, commodities or assets, we aim to reinvigorate scholarly discussions by showing how complex valuation processes can significantly mark the social life of the same cells.

A comparative ethnography of the Spanish and Ukrainian ova banking models and ova valuation regimes *Polina Vlasenko, Indiana University*; *Vincenzo Pavone, Consejo Superior Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC)*

Despite the growing transnational ova market and rapid development of ova banking, comprehensive studies on the valuation regimes of ova under different regulatory frameworks are currently lacking. This paper addresses the field’s knowledge gap by asking how the different model of ova banking in Spain and Ukraine influences the valuation of ova produced for market exchange, how this process affects the procurement and distribution of ova, the recruitment of donors, and the use of their labor. Drawing from more than 20 interviews with ARTs professionals in Spain and 70 in Ukraine this paper examines how two of the most successful models of ova valuation operate under different regulatory regimes, inside and outside the EU. While the Spanish legislation follows EU regulations and standards of quality, Ukrainian legislation is dispersed and does not regulate many important aspects of the process. The Ukrainian ova banks and clinics have adopted a more explicit business-like approach, while the Spanish market has been called (quasi) social because of the combination of a relatively attractive compensation with an altruistic frame of donation. Compared to Ukrainian unregulated market, the more regulated Spanish quasi social market seems to give private business a competitive edge. However, both market designs generate the same problems for exploitation and welfare of donors. Thus, the paper also addresses the social and economic consequences of the Spanish and Ukrainian models for both the donors and the medical professionals involved.

Custody, Care and Cost: Quantifying and Valuing Life in the Correctional Services *Andrei Guter-Sandu, LSE - London School of Economics and Political Science*; *Andrea Mennicken, LSE - London School of Economics and Political Science*

This paper examines the rise, circulation and use of “measures of the quality of prison life” (MQPL) in England and Wales. These measures were enrolled in attempts to moralize prison management by including measures of decency, dignity and rehabilitation alongside measures of security and cost. We follow these measures across different sites of prison management and investigate their implication in different, at times conflicting, quantification and valuation regimes. We unpack the complex interplay between quantification, valuation and governing by attending to the multi-faceted modalities and operations of prison performance measures – from flawed tool of representation, learning device, to powerful ammunition machine – and the conditions under which these different modalities unfold. Prison performance measures are more than faulty reflectors of what is going on. They change the way prisoners are understood and represented; they alter the capacities of agents and organizations to act and influence; and they reshape the connections and power relations they form and are embedded in. The paper examines how attempts aimed at the quantification of decency can (or cannot) contribute to the transformation of the objects of prison regulation and accountability, with particular attention to objects that are also subjects. We pay attention to the labile nature of valuation through quantification and its relationship with intertwined processes of moralization and economization. The

paper is based on six prison visits, 47 interviews with actors involved in the governing of prisoners and prison organizations as well as the study of media and parliamentary data, government and other reports.

The Economization of Early Life: Human Capital Theory and the Politics of Valuation *Zach Griffen, UCLA*

Since the concept first gained salience among economists in the mid-twentieth century, 'human capital' has most commonly been described as the economic product of 'investments' individuals make in themselves. These 'investments' are traditionally conceived of as educational in nature: in the 1960s, for example, Walter Heller of the U.S. Council of Economic Advisers posited that individuals contributed to national economic growth by pursuing additional years of higher education. More recently however, research in fields such as epigenetics and neuroscience has prompted claims that interventions made early in life—preferably before children reach age 5—produce greater returns in human capital. This is the central argument of the "Heckman Equation," a project organized around the work of economist and Nobel laureate James Heckman. Drawing on archival sources and interviews with key experts, this paper examines the historical shift in the relationship between human capital theory and social policy-making in the U.S. Whereas earlier iterations of human capital theory derived economic value primarily from the educational attainment of mature adults, in recent years the emphasis has increasingly been placed on health and development in early childhood—with some economists focusing even on in utero 'investments' by pregnant individuals to promote future economic growth. The considerable influence wielded by economists in U.S. social policy has made these forms of valuation more than academic exercises, with new forms of biopolitics emerging to promote 'early childhood investment' not just as strategies for improving individual life outcomes, but for achieving broader economic growth as well.

Valuing maintenance: The valuation of hotel housekeeping *Ville Savolainen, Tampere University*

Housekeeping has been one of the main examples of manual labour that have been outsourced to specialized companies globally. These companies have had to come up with a way to attach a steady value to this work that had previously been calculated as one expense in the wider arrangement of value-production of the spaces where cleaning is done. This presentation focuses on these practices of valuations and their relation to the role housekeeping plays in hotels' value accumulation. To valueate something intangible such as cleaning work, it must first be turned into something calculable. As cleaning is a highly subjective service product, the information obtained is always imperfect and based on grasps. The practices thus gained are not neutral, instead they impose new (temporal) standards and re-order the relations on the field where they are implemented. I juxtapose these practices to insights gained from the maintenance-studies subfield of STS, highlighting the inherent contradictions between the valuation practices and the work itself. Through this analytical lens, I aim to show 4 interrelated processes: 1) how cleaning work is turned into numbers 2) how these numbers are used to produce a financial valuation of the work, 3) the daily practices that enable the value accumulation of cleaning work and 4) how these practices relate to the role housekeeping plays in the hotels' daily life. By examining these four interrelated webs of practices, a contradictory picture emerges between the practices of care inherent in the work and its valuation.

Valuing and governing through discounting *Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech*

This paper focuses on a peculiar valuation tool called "discounting" and its troubling relations with governing and future-making. Discounting is an economic technique that derives the value of something from the flows of costs and

revenues that it is likely to generate in the future. In the process, future flows are "discounted", that is, translated into their "present value", which is claimed to be lesser because the future is imagined as distant and uncertain. Since the 1950s, discounting has become the main tool used by firms to decide which projects to invest in; concomitantly, it has been criticized for inducing short-termism and instilling the logics of financialization into managers' mundane operations. Discounting has also gradually spread into policy making, as part of cost benefit analysis. It has been criticized, in particular in climate change, environmental and health policies, for its inability to engage with the long-term and its disturbing valuations of human life. Drawing on a broader research project on the historical sociology of discounting, I propose to delve into the relationship between valuing and governing as instrumented by discounting. I will use several examples, drawn from the justification of environmental regulation, the pricing of drugs, and current debates on Covid lockdowns and the value of lives saved, to tease out the implications of discounting on the ways in which the future is conceived and acted upon, and discuss the conundrums raised by attempts at governing things and people by valuing them.

Session Organizers:

Kristin Asdal, TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture

Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech

Chair:

Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna

087. Seeds for a Planthropocene: Growing Good Relations among Plants and People II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

If the Anthropocene is a bad scene that grows capital and conquest, and stages unlivable relations among people and more-than-human kin, what methods, modes of attention, and tactics do we need to stage relations otherwise? Can we learn to grow solidarities rather than disparities? This double panel explores ways that people stage relations with plants in order to offer generative grounds for reimagining the relations that can grow livable worlds. The papers speculate on ways of seeding Planthropocenes, that is, activating scenes in which people form solidarities with plants as a means to seed good relations. Planthropocene thinking, which displaces the self-aggrandizing human, and centres a collective, hybrid entity composed of plants and people, attunes us to forms of growth that are not about growing markets or expanding capitalist production. As artists, practitioners and researchers we weave together stories about plants and people from the Global North and South, engaging anticolonial and decolonial frameworks to reckon with ways of doing plant/people relations differently. The papers explore the promises portended by vegetally-engulfed ruins in Cambodia, resistances to the toxic foundations of green development in Mauritius, the activist artworks of the Lawn (Re)Disturbance Laboratory in NY, a vegetable patch on stolen land in Toronto, efforts in feral viticulture to re-wild grapes, a praxis for attuning our feral bodies to plants and fungi, practices that support artists' dialogues with plants, plant/people intimacies among Indigenous elders and their allies in South Africa, and the unseen relations of seeds in the wake of seed monopolies.

Participants:

Plant-building assemblages and the potential of "ruins" *Aadita Chaudhury, York University*

Ta Prohm, a 12th-century Buddhist temple located in the historical city of Angkor outside of present-day Siem Reap, in Cambodia, is famously enveloped by large rainforest tree roots that are integral to its iconic visual and affective appeal. Similarly, just across the Indian Ocean, ruins of the buildings in the Ross Island Penal Colony in the Andaman and Nicobar Islands have become engulfed by the island's native trees and vines. What can this slow vegetal disruption of some consciously-arranged order of stone, adobe, brick, or concrete

reveal to us? What ways of being that emerge at the fresh, respective intersections of spiritual and colonial placemaking? Architecture, through its material-semiotic ability to terraform living spaces and places, has always been used to create and cement particular socio-cultural and moral economies. As architectural design can cement and privilege certain modes of being and hierarchies of social arrangement, the unsettling of these forms by vegetal life raises questions about the new worlds being birthed and refracted through these plant-building assemblages found across so-called 'ruins'. As ruins overtaken by plants have long been seen as charismatic apocalyptic portents (Myers), this paper presents a provocation to think of world-endings otherwise - away from colonial framings of apocalypse (Mitchell & Chaudhury). By considering the architecture of plant-building assemblages as substrates for new worlds, as a rupture from colonial space-time scales and imaginaries, I offer insights into the co-creative processes that occur in overlooked voids, leftover spaces, and places of 'decay' - and explore how they foreshadow emergent orders of being.

Resisting Toxic 'Growth'? Cultivating good relations amid toxic legacies of green development *Jessica Caporusso, York University*

In the small island-nation of Mauritius, rising tensions over energy security, petrochemicals, and the environment have coalesced around the preservation of toxic systems of 'growth.' One such exploit centers on the recuperation of both sugarcane, a plant rooted in legacies of colonial plantation violence, and *Arundo Donax*, a native plant marked 'weed,' into sustainable biofuels. This restaging of sugarcane and *Arundo* as future-forward 'technologies' emphasizes the reproductive capacities of plants as photosynthesizers, while overshadowing enduring legacies of colonial botanical knowledge that undergird this transformation. A second is the re-skilling of factory and field workers in the wake of the local sugar industry's near collapse and subsequent downsizing. Here, labourers are trained in the use of chemical rooting hormones and fertilizers to maximize plant propagation, in the process, reinscribing toxic models of forced productivity. These practices stand in contrast to more responsive bioremediation technologies simultaneously happening in Mauritius, including vermiculture, which, while not premised on such expansionist thinking, must still contend with 'growth'-centred logics. Drawing from ethnographic fieldwork, this paper examines how material processes and social relations extend toxic patterns of 'good' growth, where goodness stands in for fecundity as opposed to living well together. Further, it questions if and how good relations can be cultivated out of toxic production systems, without presuming that growth can be wholly excised from injurious foundations. This paper thus foregrounds more than the possibility of surviving toxic systems, to reconsider how to live in good relation with plants, chemicals, and landscapes amid toxicity.

Contested Turf: Exploring Phytocentric Pedagogies with the Lawn (Re)Disturbance Laboratory *Ellie Irons, The Next Epoch Seed Library/Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute*

The living land currently known as Troy, New York, is subject to antiquated mandates declaring any growth of "weeds" to a height over six inches to be a "nuisance, injurious to public interests and public health." This mandate encourages humans who steward open land to default to regular mowing, co-creating a mosaic of closely shorn vegetation throughout the city. Framing Troy's ubiquitous lawns as perpetually disturbed habitats, The Lawn (Re)Disturbance Laboratory uses public sculpture to suspend lawn maintenance, allowing other possibilities to emerge. In dialogue with a rich history of lawn-disrupting artistic practices, and responding to key concepts in feminist and Indigenous science studies, the project centers plant agency by turning to seeds lying dormant in the soil for guidance (Myers, Todd). By removing and composting one by one-meter patches of turf and protecting them with sculptures, we defer to the

creative vigor of the soil seed bank. As white settler artists working on Mohican and Lenape land on Turtle Island, we acknowledge our complicity and responsibility in grappling with the colonial environmental management regimes that produce lawns and the weedy, often unwelcome plants who disrupt them (Haraway, Shotwell). Through sculptural interventions, vegetal attunement exercises, and community science activities, we explore a kind of phytocentric pedagogy that is indebted to feminist and Indigenous pedagogies (Bang, hooks, la paperson), offering the friction laden and rewarding process of learning from and with weedy plants as one means of cultivating plant-human solidarity in damaged landscapes (Stoetzer, Tsing).

Gardening Otherwise: Teachings from a Pandemic Garden on Stolen Land *Natasha Myers, York University*

What is your garden growing? I pose this question to people staging relations with plants in laboratories, artists' studios, botanical gardens, ecological restoration sites, and city parks. Rather than an inventory of plants grown, this question asks about the relationships a given garden nourishes. In addition to the relations among plants, people, and the more-than-human community of a garden's immediate surround, it is important to ask: How does a given garden grow capitalism? How does it grow dispossession? And importantly: What else could a garden grow? This paper reflects on a small vegetable garden I planted in the early days of the COVID-19 pandemic as a "making and doing" project: a site for experimenting with protocols for seeding a Planthropocene, a scene that aims to seed plant/people solidarities. Planthropocene worlding demands a reckoning with and transformation of the relations between plants and people set in motion by colonialism and capitalism. This paper asks: how do conventional gardens grow racial capitalism, settler common sense (e.g. Gilmore; Lethabo King; Tuck and Yang) and other unlivable relations? Situated in Toronto on Dish With One Spoon Treaty lands, my garden grows on razed oak savannahs and corn fields that have been sites for Indigenous subsistence, sovereignty, and ceremony for generations. The property enclosure of this garden and the demographics of the neighborhood are also clear markers of the legacies of plantation agriculture that spatialize whiteness and wealth (McKittrick) in urban home gardens like this one. This paper asks: Can we garden otherwise?

Session Organizer:

Natasha Myers, York University

Chair:

Deborah Heath, Lewis and Clark College

Discussant:

Kristina Lyons, University of Pennsylvania

088. (Re)configuring care practices in pandemic times III

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Care practices were addressed in STS by Annemarie Mol (2002, 2008, 2010) as capturing a specific way of engaging with material reality as well as framing situated human relations. Hence, care bears not only upon intimacy or affectivity, but relates to forms of interdependency between ontology and normativity ("ontonorms"; Mol 2012). The session starts from and further develops the discussions on relevance of care practices focussing on the (re)configurations of care practices during the COVID-19 pandemic. Such a discussion of „care“ takes up not only a currently highly relevant social topic, but also acknowledges the salient empirical shaping of theoretical reflections on care in STS as ways of handling reality and transforming social relations. While COVID-19 differently addresses virologists, clinicians, physicists, epidemiologists, immunologists, or economists (Mol and Hardon 2020), a wide range of practices of care proliferated in response to the health crisis beyond these formal and mainstream settings, draw mainly on spatial (and social) proximity (neighbourhoods, peer-groups), and emphasised a temporal continuity of the caring engagement (regular visits, extended homeschooling). In a word:

specific (re)configurations of care are rendered visible in dealing with personal concern, vulnerability, and (inter)dependence (Kittay 2015). The session includes contributions on: – expertise negotiated along care practices; – care related to groups traditionally framed as disadvantaged: elderly, people with disabilities, indigenous people, and other culturally diverse groups; – goods shaping actors understanding of care; – alliances of human and non-human entities as modes of pragmatic coping with pandemic crisis; – methodological adjustments regarding (re)configurations of care.

Participants:

Communities in Isolation: the Digital Escape of "Reality Shifting" *Sara Bimo, York University*

Over the course of the COVID-19 pandemic the phenomenon of "reality shifting"—the practice of inserting oneself into an alternate reality through intense meditation—gained immense popularity on TikTok. Dedicated communities have since popped up on a number of social media sites, and serve as places where believers can share their experiences and gain tips on how to "shift." While many claim that reality shifting has given them a way to escape the trauma of the current moment, some users have also pointed out the isolating effects of the practice. In this project, I undertake a digital ethnography of 3 "reality shifting" communities on TikTok, Reddit, and Youtube in order to examine the curious subculture that has developed around the trend. I trace the rise of reality shifting gurus; users who claim to have mastered the practice, and hold cult-like influence over their followers. Through this research, I shed light on the importance of meditative spiritual practices in fostering community bonds in times of crisis, but also highlight the ways that rising levels of paranoia and conspiracy theory in digital spaces reduce the efficacy of self care practices and transform spaces of care into insular communities characterized by strict hierarchy and conformism. Ultimately, this project aims to explore questions related to the efficacy of therapeutic practices in our precarious digital age: in an time where many seek closeness, connection, and community online, how can we ensure that unregulated communities are providing meaningful support rather than exacerbating existing mental health issues?

COVIDsomnia: Sleep Care in Pandemic Times *Nico Wettmann, Justus Liebig University of Giessen*

Individual and social crises are frequently related to sleep. Sleep is thus seen as a treatment for such crises, for example, to cope with diseases. Otherwise, as behavior disrupted by the crisis, known as sleep problems and disorders. A historical view of the medicalization of sleep shows that it was the pandemic conditions of their time – the Spanish flu or avian influenza – that turned the medical gaze on sleep. Constructed as an object of knowledge, sleep appeared observable with medical instruments and thus manipulable: with the right sleep hygiene, »good« sleep could then be obtained. The current state of pandemic also makes sleep and dream changes tangible and brings sleep into the social consciousness. Without any medical equipment being needed, digital self-tracking apps can be used to easily measure, evaluate and regulate sleep as an everyday practice. Quantitative and visualized sleep data and bodily-somatic perceptions then make sleep not only experiential but also evaluable and re-formulate quality sleep as well as poor sleep. Sleep care is no longer just a topic in the medical-scientific field but is also being explored in private areas of life. Sleep trackers measure their own sleep, experiment with their data, and engage in discussions in online forums. Through empirical cases of online discussions, I will present first reflections on the digital knowledge production of sleep trackers and show the problematization of sleep and the implications of »good« sleep in the light of the COVID-19 pandemic.

Everyday (self)caring during the pandemic: results of CUIDAR study *Sebastian Rojas Navarro, Universidad Andres Bello; Samanta Alarcon Arcos, Pontificia Universidad Católica de*

Chile; Maria Alejandra Energici, Universidad Alberto Hurtado; Nicolas Schongut-Grollmus, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

Worldwide, governments have implemented several policies aimed at containing the dissemination of the COVID-19 pandemic. In Chile, the government followed the example of countries such as Italy, forcing massive lockdowns, closing educational institutions, and encouraging social distancing and work from home. This has affected certain caring needs commonly met outside of the home, which now relied on the household for their satisfaction, modifying how they work. Once the webs of interdependence sustaining the everyday caring practices that we need become discontinuous, or are simply cut clean, how does this alter and modify how care is enacted, experienced, and understood within the households? The aim of this presentation is two-folded: First, it highlights the potentialities arising from an approach to care under the lens provided by STS scholarship. Secondly, we share some results of CUIDAR, a survey about care forms, times, and spaces of care conducted in Chile regarding the effects of the pandemic on everyday caring practices within the households. Responded by over 2000 individuals all over the country, CUIDAR reveals the significant role that spatialities and materialities play in caring, and how—during the pandemic—care has become more evident for those who give, receives, and need it.

Care, Objects and the Domestic Space through the Covid-19 Pandemic *Alicia Márquez Murrieta, Instituto de Investigaciones Dr. José María Luis Mora*

In Mexico, in March 2020, the government's slogan facing the Covid-19 pandemic was "stay at home", without using the coercive measures as in other parts of the world and calling for a certain "citizen and healthy civility". Also, from that moment the classes of millions of students from preschool to university became online or through various technological devices such as televisions or community radios; as well, many of the "non-essential" paid work continued but it has to be done from home. These are only some of the consequences of the pandemic crisis that has been going on for almost a year, with different moments of intensity due to the colour of the "traffic light" (semáforo, a measure to indicate the gravity of the situation). The pressure that this crisis has brought to the domestic environment and in particular to women, has added to the inequality in care that existed before the pandemic in the country. This has led to important reorganizations of the domestic space where both objects and people have had to find new reciprocal adjustments. I am interested in reflecting on those adjustments, that I suppose have been changing over time; and crossing them closely with the theme of care that, following Batthyány (2020), has a relational aspect. In addition, the idea of care has to do with the transversality of the practices and representations defined as feminine and it seeks to realize that the material and immaterial, public and private, the physical and emotional, go hand in hand and are significantly interwoven dimensions (Carrasco, Borderías and Torns, 2011, cited by Batthyány, 2020). But it is also important to reflect on how these distinctions are constantly reconfigured and how the months that the pandemic has lasted have come to disrupt the canonical definitions of these spaces and with it, practices, relationships between people and with the environment and objects, have also been modified. In this sense, I will be interested in tracking how the ways of assembling between objects, people, spaces and their relationship with health and care has not been the same over time. In the work I am interested in discussing in a particular way one of the six dimensions that Carol Thomas proposes when researching or debating the multidimensional concept of care (2011): the institutional framework and the physical location in which care is presented (Thomas in Batthyány, p. 42) and how this dimension has impacts on others, for example, the identities of caregivers and recipients of care. In this sense, we could use the literature on

categorization processes and categorical pairs. The material will be the use of my own experience, in a kind of auto-ethnography and comments made by people on Facebook pages. In addition, I will conduct interviews.

Session Organizer:

Cristina Popescu, EHESS - Centre d'Etude des Mouvements Sociaux

Discussant:

Stefan Nicolae, University of Trier

089. Aging with other-than-humans: STS and age studies beyond technological solutions

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

In recent years, Science and Technology studies have paid increasing attention to ageing and elderly care. At the cross-road with critical age studies, new areas and theoretical developments such as socio-gerontechnology or material gerontology are making important contributions. Informed by material-semiotics, post-humanism, and affect theory these developments are shedding light on the critical role of materiality and other-than-human beings in the constitution of old age as a social construct and bio-political device. They show how notions of ageing well (such as active ageing or successful ageing) are materialised in technological and biomedical innovations and how these configure modes of doing age in older's people daily-life. Drawing on the more-than-human turn in STS and age studies, this panel is an invitation to extend the reach of these developments beyond their traditional focus on innovative digital and biomedical "solutions" for the ageing society. We invite papers that consider more-than-human entanglements with animal, plants, buildings, landscapes, etc. in critical studies of age and elderly care. We also look for contributions that delve into the politics of relations in these more-than-human entanglements in later life. The panel is an invitation to consider questions such as: How elderly care is reconfigured when care is not considered from anthropocentric visions? What does ageing and old age become when ageing is seen as a stage of becoming-with other-than-humans? How do other-than-human ageing and elderly care matter in these entanglements? What notions of ageing well and good elderly care emerge as a result of this?

Participants:

Aging-with Many: Conceptualizing Ecologies Of Care In The Field Of Ambient Assisted Living *Hannah Gruen, Helmut Schmidt University Hamburg*

Over two decades, Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) technologies and smart living environments have been presented as both solutions to care deficits and possibilities for self-determination in older person's daily life. In these AAL scenarios, 'the home' is not only stressed as a pivotal element for good future elderly care practices but as 'the ambient' that must be technologically equipped, architecturally rebuilt and innovatively inter-connected with others – technologies, interfaces, sensors, atmospheres, neighborhoods, families, medical infrastructures, maintenance services, etcetera (e.g., Sánchez-Criado et al. 2014; Oudshoorn 2011). Accepting the more-than-human turn in STS and critical age studies as an invitation to work less anthropocentric through questions of care and technologies in later life, I suggest taking 'the ambient' and its affective, socio-material and spatial dimensions as a starting point for future research on AAL (e.g., Pols 2019, 2017). While some works concentrate on practices through which specific notions of aging and caring well are materialized in, with and through AAL innovations (e.g., Endter 2017), others implicitly concern 'the ambient' in drawing on ecological concepts: infrastructure, ecology, technogeography, technoecology or assemblage (e.g., Star & Ruhleder 1994; Haraway 2008; Puig de la Bellacasa 2016; Danholt & Langstrup 2012; Lorenz-Meyer et al. 2019; Schwennesen 2019). In this paper, I first discuss prominent ecological concepts flourishing in STS and link them to more spatial and geographical approaches. I then conceptualize an

ecologies of care perspective for a specific multiple-case study design that contributes to reconfigure elderly care and self-determination in urban, more-than-human AAL entanglements.

Infrastructures of Voice, Environments of Affect & Intimacy:

Voice-based Technology and Older People *Marie Ermer, IT University of Copenhagen; Stina Jørgensen, IT University of Copenhagen; Signe Yndigegn, Design Department, IT University, Copenhagen*

Voice-enabled technology has been celebrated as a breakthrough in eldercare. Mainstream discourses emphasize voice-based technology as practical assistants, and thus figure voice as a practical means to achieve certain ends. But there is more to voice interactions than merely distributing messages and articulating commands. Voice-based interactions create sonic environments, enact affect, identities, likes and dislikes. The paper explores the co-existence of older people and voice-based technologies ethnographically, and through the STS concept of infrastructure and a cultural anthropological view on voice. We see infrastructures as both objects and the relations between objects (Larkin), as 'complex chains of material relations' that 'reconfigure bodies, societies [...] knowledge and discourses in ways often unnoticed' (Harvey, Jensen and Morita). Voice is both a sonic material phenomenon and a culturally elaborated metaphor (Weidman), which connects deeply to feelings of intimacy, identity and community. Voice-based interactions can thus be seen as infrastructures that link the realms of the technical, cultural and sociopolitical to the level of the individual, creating sites where shared discourses and values, affect, and aesthetics are made manifest in and contested through embodied and material practice. With the increasing co-existence of older people and voice-based assistants, we see a need for ethnographic views on what these technologies are, how they can be studied, and what they do. We develop the notion of 'infrastructures of voice and affect' as a more-than-human approach to study entanglements of ageing, environments of affect and intimacy, and voice-based technology.

The benevolence of nature for frail humans in a disrupted world

Cornelia Hummel, Université de Genève

In March 2020, 25 elderly people living in Western Switzerland were invited to write "Confinement diaries" for three or more months, in order to document their everyday life during the Swiss confinement. While everyone is under the "stay at home" reign, while elderly people are particularly struggling with isolation and the pressure to use technology to keep in touch with family and friends, the pages of the diaries are full of trees, flowers, blue skies, sweet rays of sunshine, the soothing view of mountains through a window. Our writers look at the colours, hear the birds, smell the flowers and the young leaves; they receive "the beauty of the nature" as a free and safe gift over which the virus has no control. Situated at the intersection between sociology of aging and STS, this paper will explore care and the benevolence of nature as non-human actor in the life of elderly people, during the confinement and more generally.

Becoming-old with a dog: Human-animal entanglements in later

life transitions *Nete Schwennesen, Copenhagen University; Daniel Lopez Gomez, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya*

The research agenda at the intersection of STS and gerontology is very much dominated by technological innovation and therefore by human-made artifacts such as digital devices, objects and buildings. Other-than-human-living beings seem to be absent in this agenda. This is quite striking as people not only age-in-place with technologies and mundane objects and artifacts but also, and increasingly, closely entangled with pet animals. Based on two stories from our ongoing fieldwork on ageing and care in Denmark and in Spain, we explore how human-dog entanglements affect and are affected by the older adults transition to new housing and care collectives such as nursing homes and senior co-housing. Depending on how dogs become

entangled in these collectives, not only the transition of their human-owner can be hampered or eased, but also the dog's transition to old age and the very definition of the collective itself. As both stories illustrate, when dogs become part of a care collective, pertinent questions are raised about who or what belongs to the collective and is to be taken care of. Moreover, we highlight how older adults living their lives closely entangled with animals shed new light on ageing as a process that humans share with other living beings, which over time constitutes new forms of vulnerability and needs of care that cut across species.

Session Organizers:

Daniel Lopez Gomez, Universitat Oberta de Catalunya
Nete Schwennesen, Copenhagen University

090. Enclosing Ecologies: Infrastructures in Greenhouse Worlds

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Living organisms, like plants or 'resources' like water, appearing in the past in the margins of ethnographies are now taken to the center of our enquiries, providing a new focus on the complex milieu of infrastructures as a multi-species encounter. This panel thinks further multi-species relationality and the value of food within greenhouses ecologies. It is urgent to analyze the socio-environmental effects of greenhouses horticultural systems –even more given the pressure of EU to 1) move to a plant-based diet (Lancet, 2019) and; 2) increase horticultural productivity in Europe, (specially in South Spain); and 3) maximize resources to reduce agricultural ecological impact. The greenhouse complex, in addition, needs to be analyzed as a historical process pertaining to specific transformations of 'naturecultures' (Haraway, 2016) where socio-environmental processes are inevitably entangled. How is horticultural production transforming socio-environmental processes and relations? While population increase demands more production, such demand clashes with a narrative of resource scarcity. Both futures (the future of food and the future of resource availability) are in tension. The aim of this panel is to explore the different ways in which to study entangled greenhouse ecologies, working in messy sites, and how to articulate complexity. This is particularly important considering histories of colonial plantations, monocropping, and forced mobilities. This perspective would help to make visible the relevance of STS to understand ecologies and multispecies entanglements that challenge taken for granted attitudes towards technified agricultural sites as 'controlled' environments.

Participants:

Greenhouses Inside Out: The flows in Spanish Almerian Greenhouse Production *Trine My Thygaard-Nielsen, dept of Anthropology, Aarhus University*

Greenhouse ecologies are often considered controllable enclosed spaces without historical contexts, easily constructed in hostile places such as cavities in between high-rises or in desert areas in order to efficiently provide food for a growing population. Building on ethnographic fieldwork conducted with various actors in the mainstream greenhouse production in the Almerian region of Southern Spain, this presentation challenges these views. It discusses how greenhouse ecologies are dynamic places formed by and forming their surroundings. Indeed, in an area appointed by the Franco regime as *zona de interés nacional* [national zone of interest] and rapidly developed through colonial politics, political ambitions and poverty, history is essential when understanding the context specific peculiarities of greenhouse ecologies as they emerged in Southern Spain. Such peculiarities continue today in the everyday management of e.g. resource management and low input methods. Although greenhouses locally are often described as enclosed spaces, these descriptions exist side by side with the many (uncontrolled) out- and inflows taking place in the everyday life. Wildlife, domesticated life and weather are concrete examples of visiting local elements, while changing climates and policies are less tangible but nonetheless entanglements playing their parts in the maintenance and development of industrial greenhouse ecologies. All of which are important aspects to consider in the debate on how to increase

productivity in Southern Spain.

Planetary Circuits: to Channel Greenhouse Metabolic Flows
Filippo Bertoni, Aarhus University

As ecological catastrophe looms large on the horizon, the salvation promised by ecomodernism invariably passes through an intensification of agriculture and its caloric and metabolic extractivism – and becomes gospel in the centres of technocratic administration. This near future is commonly framed by the interfacing of greenhouse technologies and architectures with the system control engineering of industrial ecology: future agriculture – both terrestrial and interplanetary – seems to always pivot around the enclosure of the greenhouse and its relatives. To explore these futures and their different presents, this presentation offers a guided tour weaving together the hortus conclusus of the ancien régime, the imperial expansion of monocrop plantations, the high-tech agriculture of the Dutch Food Valley, and the dystopian visions of Soyent-based diets and their brood. Through genre-bending stories of agricultural futures and pasts, the circuitry of these metabolic landscapes becomes apparent, revealing the recurring frictions that structure these infrastructural imaginaries of the planet. As an experiment in narrative STS, the presentation offers insights on these historical and speculative constellations of future agriculture, as well as opening some possible alternatives for what they can mean for the social studies of science.

Back to the Glasshouse Future *Josh Cohen*

This presentation reflects on the movement of some of Europe's most popular warmer climate houseplants from South Africa into Europe from early colonial periods until the present day. These stories highlight a few of the ways in which the development of glass and heating technologies and their use in private, public and commercial ships, homes and gardens has been intertwined with the mass arrival of these ecology-transforming phyto-beings. Larger windows, central heating systems and so on - in many cases deriving directly out of technologies developed for the rich and their expensive, exoticized greenhouse plant collections, have become expected constituents of homes across Europe and the colder, wealthier world in general. In this way, it could be argued, 'greenhouse ecologies' include the homes - and actual greenhouses and conservatories! - humanity (or some of us) already live in, with plants or without. On the one hand, this presentation will consider entanglements between 21st century pressures to increase food production, climate change, population growth, and earlier periods of the 'greenhousing' of the world. On the other, it proposes this figure of our (already) greenhoused world as a tool for critical reflection on some of the potential social-ecological-material consequences of hyper-productive, greenhoused agricultural techno-futures.

Taxonomies of Exclusion: The Categorical Work of Building Worlds Without Worlds *Pierre du Plessis*

Greenhouses are both world-building and world-destroying devices that create habitable environments within spaces that are otherwise inhospitable to the ecologies they host. They create worlds within worlds. Doing so has involved concentrated taxonomical work that does not just classify plant species, for instance, but creates the conditions for their extraction and the production of particular kinds of landscapes: landscapes of enclosure. In this sense, greenhouses also cut worlds off from worlds, often imitating the colonial and postcolonial environments that have been most violently extracted. While this has enabled the production of plants in places distant from those species' natural habitats through the creation of artificial environments, entire relational ecologies have been reordered through the logics of enclosure and exclusion. This paper considers the politics of enclosure –together with enclosure—to explore the effects that the proliferation of artificial greenhouses environments have on the distant ecologies they seek to imitate. It asks, how do greenhouses replicate the colonial processes that

destroy the environments they now seek to recreate through logics of enclosure and enclosure?

Water Flows: 'Greenhouse Composites' in the Netherlands and Spain *Rebeca Ibáñez Martín, Humanities Cluster, Dutch Academy of Science (KNAW)*

As the world population continues to increase, a pressing question is 'how to feed the world'. The European Union is pressing to move to a plant-based diet. This is not an easy task: pressure to increase horticultural productivity in Europe, and to maximize recourses to reduce agricultural ecological impact, poses a complex riddle. In Europe the hotspots for horticulture production are the Netherlands (Westland region) and Spain (Almeria and Murcia). Both draw on similar 'controlled environments' (greenhouses), and deal with water, waste, waste water, crops, and labour as resources to be managed. Intensive horticultural infrastructures shape the future of water, unevenly distributes who has access to water, produce new mobilities of goods, and also of people, in many different capacities, and in doing so shape how water is known and what water can do (Swyngedouw et al., 2002). This paper focuses on water worlds and water knowledge circulations in each region. How does greenhouses affect the use and distribution of water in each region? Water use and distribution generate tensions – When and why is water prioritized for horticulture or for urban development? What is more, wastewater management highlights how difficult it is to control or do a 'bordering' of water. The effects of water leaks are perceived far away, in a contaminated canal or in a eutrophication event (e.g. the disaster of the Mar Menor, in Murcia). While some ecological areas die, others are kept alive. This paper would help to make visible the relevance of STS to understand ecological entanglements that challenge taken for granted attitudes towards technified agricultural sites as 'controlled' environments.

Session Organizer:

Rebeca Ibáñez Martín, Humanities Cluster, Dutch Academy of Science (KNAW)

091. Gay Genes in the Post-genomic Era

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

In a landmark 2019 Science paper, geneticist Andrea Ganna and his multidisciplinary team's "genome-wide association study" (GWAS) identified five loci of genetic material associated with same-sex sexual activity among a large American and British sample of people of European ancestry. Unlike its own ancestors, the post-genomics paradigm appears able and willing to account for much of the complexity and contingency that queer scholars have long chastised the science of sexuality for sidelining. As such, it is now the task of STS scholars to similarly complicate the epistemic foundations of those efforts to isolate and analyze the slippery specimen of desire. In this roundtable, we take up this task from a variety of perspectives informed by our distinct (inter)disciplinary orientations and methods, from close reading to political economy and discourse analysis. We ask: what is happening in the study itself, where did it come from, and where is it going? Ultimately, we suggest that the post-genomic paradigm demonstrates most is the power, romance, and tenacity of biologically-infllected visions of human behavior and identity. Even when the natural sciences offer more fluid, less strictly-deterministic accounts of queer modes of being, their voice continues to be one among the most authoritative on sex and sexuality's nature and origins. In this roundtable, each presenter will give brief (~7 minute) provocations followed by a moderated discussion. We aim to stimulate questions and discursive answers to the place(s) of critical STS scholarship in the discourse on post-genomic sexualities and sexual epigenetics.

Presenters:

Stephanie Clare, University of Washington

Patrick R Grzanka, The University of Tennessee

Joanna Wuest, Princeton University

Kevin M. Moseby, Drexel University

Session Organizer:

Patrick R Grzanka, The University of Tennessee

Chair:

Tom Waidzunus, Temple University

092. The social and political features of biomedical innovation in pandemic times

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Biomedical innovation is situated within the political, economic and social landscape that is continually changing. STS has uniquely attended to how social actors (scientists, clinicians, patients, regulators and funders) engaged in biomedical innovation respond to, struggle with, accommodate to and even resist those social and political forces. The coronavirus pandemic of 2020 required unprecedented coordinated feats of biomedical innovation, to test, monitor, treat, cure and prevent what we now call COVID-19. The scope of this crisis prompted some to challenge long-established features of scientific innovation around privacy, ownership and ethics – to mobilize biomedical research to address a global public health crisis. These calls have the potential to challenge long-established features of the competitive landscape of biomedical innovation within global capitalism; however it is not clear if these calls to re-imagine science challenged, shifted or perhaps entrenched practices and beliefs that underscore the production of scientific evidence. This panel will examine how COVID-19 affected relations between social actors engaged in biomedical innovation. What are "good" relations in this context; how do "partners" in research share and disseminate data equitably and justly amid the competing pulls of a global public health crisis, and the economic competitiveness that is ingrained in biomedical innovation? This session considers empirical work on actors engaged in the organization and execution clinical trials and vaccine dissemination amid COVID-19. It also examines theoretical and historical concepts underpinning regulation and funding of biomedical innovation, and seeks to examine the assumptions, practices and challenges of biomedical innovation amid a global pandemic.

Participants:

The social arrangements that shape vaccine hesitancy *Maya Goldenberg, Associate Professor, Department of Philosophy, University of Guelph*

Recent scholarship on vaccine hesitancy has challenged the common view that people who resist vaccines are scientifically uninformed or anti-science, arguing instead that vaccine hesitancy signals a crisis of trust between the publics and the institutions that structure civic life. More concretely, public resistance to vaccines is a demand for institutional structures and governance that are responsive to issues of justice and equity (Goldenberg 2021). This insight comes from study of pediatric vaccine hesitancy in industrialized nations, yet the global pivot to COVID vaccination, and the presence of COVID vaccine hesitancy, bring new priority to equity and justice concerns regarding vaccination practices and how they support public health more generally. These equity and justice concerns will be examined with reference to COVID vaccine hesitancy and refusal among front-line health care workers in the first phase of vaccine rollouts in many industrialized nations (Solomon et al. 2021). Goldenberg, Maya J. *Vaccine Hesitancy: Public Trust, Expertise, and the War on Science*. Pittsburgh: University of Pittsburgh Press. Solomon, Erika et al. "Vaccine Scepticism Among Medics Sparks Alarm in Europe and US." *Financial Times*, January 8, 2021. <https://www.ft.com/content/c576e15f-e5b1-4369-a5f0-073b4466036f>

Cooperation and competition: The composition of clinical trial partnerships evaluating convalescent plasma for COVID-19 *Quinn Grundy, University of Toronto*

Clinical trials of convalescent plasma for treatment of COVID-19 bring together competing stakeholders in order to address scarcity of plasma donors and trial participants. The two main treatment approaches – transfusion and manufacture into a "hyperimmune" immunoglobulin – involve two different, but

often overlapping and competing groups of stakeholders. Researchers, clinicians, and funders must partner with licensed, publicly funded and often nationally coordinated blood services to collect plasma for transfusion. These services are in competition with the for-profit plasma industry, which recruits and remunerates donors in order to manufacture of plasma products. The scarcity of donors and participants is exacerbated by regulatory climates, which have allowed access to convalescent plasma outside of clinical trials, and political and celebrity hype of the benefits of convalescent plasma in the popular press. Clinical trials of convalescent plasma thus, provide a case study to understand the larger political economy in which clinical trials are conducted, which historically incentivizes the rapid proliferation and dissemination of ‘positive’ trials and often disincentivizes collaboration and the sharing of scarce resources and trial data (Fisher, 2008). This case also allows exploration of the regulation, use and distribution of human biological materials within capitalist economies that support techno-scientific innovation and market expansion around blood and blood products (Farrell, 2012). We turn critical attention to the composition and nature of clinical trials partnerships and the implications of various models of clinical trials governance for research integrity and the distribution of public goods, including clinical trials data and allocation of potential treatments. References Farrell, A.-M. (2012). *The Politics of Blood: Ethics, Innovation and the Regulation of Risk*. Cambridge, MA: Cambridge University Press. Fisher, J. A. (2008). *Medical Research for Hire: The Political Economy of Pharmaceutical Clinical Trials*. New Brunswick, NJ: Rutgers University Press.

Sponsoring medicines before, during, and after Covid19

Matthew Herder, Director, Health Law Institute, Associate Professor, Faculties of Medicine and Law, Dalhousie University

Spawning catastrophic change, Covid19 has also reproduced the status quo in important domains, including the field of pharmaceutical drugs, biologics, and vaccines. Replicating a pattern of public subsidy leading to private control observed in biomedical research for the past several decades, unprecedented levels of government funding have been allocated to the firms racing to develop interventions capable of detecting, treating, and preventing SARS-CoV-2 with few strings attached to ensure data transparency, equitable access, or affordable pricing. While public and private interests have long been intertwined in the development of medicines, in this paper I trace the concept of a medicine “sponsor”—the “good relations” it has configured through its integration into biopharmaceutical law and policy during the twentieth century—in order to renew questions about how biopharmaceutical research is financed; how knowledge about these interventions is best generated; why manufacturing capacity has become so consolidated; and, ultimately, whether the current system of medicines production adequately serves the public good. Drawing upon insights from “law and political economy” scholarship, I argue that if the dominant neoliberal approach to medicines production is to be undone in the wake of Covid19, redistributive aims and mechanisms must be read into both the intellectual property practices that sit behind the development of most medicines, and the standards against which they are regulated.

The political economy of plasma in the COVID era *Kelly Holloway, University of Toronto*

In the past 50 years, plasma has become a lifesaving medical treatment, and a global industry. Plasma is the protein-rich liquid portion of blood that helps other blood components circulate throughout the body. It is used to create plasma protein therapies through a process called fractionation, and these therapies have played a vital role in the management of various immunological disorders. As demand for plasma increases globally, blood operators are developing strategies to increase plasma collection to meet this demand. This effort raises questions about how to

manage the increased demand for clinical uses of plasma; how to increase self-sufficiency of domestic supply; and how to navigate tensions inherent in the interactions between public and private entities working together to provide a medical product. These questions have been compounded and complicated by COVID-19. This paper presents findings from a case study of Canadian Blood Services’ effort to increase self-sufficiency of domestic supply of plasma for the production of plasma derived products for Canadians. Inspired by the political economy of research and innovation (Tyfield et al 2017), it situates the various actors – donors, recipients of plasma therapies, scientists, regulators, blood collection agencies, fractionation industry, as a part of a complex whole. This theoretical framework will draw attention to the social and cultural dimensions of the production of knowledge about plasma products, the political economic dimensions of the collection and distribution of plasma, and power relations that shape these dynamics. Tyfield, D., Lave, R., Randalls, S., & Thorpe, C. (Eds.). (2017). *The routledge handbook of the political economy of science*. Taylor & Francis.

Session Organizer:

Kelly Holloway, University of Toronto

093. Neuro-gender-literacies in the making: assembling new forms of critical engagement with neuroscientific research

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Organized by members of the international Neurogenderings Network, this meet-up aims to present and collect emerging ideas on “neuro-gender-literacies.” We aspire to create new forms of critical technoscience engagement on the way conceptions of gender, race and class are reified in neuroscientific research, through the circulation of neuro-facts, and by neurotechnological developments. Neuro-gender-literacies follow a methodology for interactive and dynamically developing approaches that should improve competencies to assess, reflect, debate and generate neuroscientific research and neurotechnology, based on knowledge of their socio-cultural, intersectional and colonial embeddedness and their impacts on human lives. The plural “literacies” is meant to invoke the multiple fields that benefit from and take part in new forms of technoscience engagement, such as laboratory scientists, psychologists, policy makers, teachers and students, and the public. In this meet-up, we gather interested scholars, discuss our approaches, test ideas and spark collaborations by means of: - presenting new forms of critical engagement with neuroscience research and neurotechnology, - gathering scholars from various disciplines to brainstorm about new formats for neuro-gender-literacies, - offering bigger and smaller break-out rooms on different literacies, such a room on neuro-gender literacies in the laboratory and a room on speculative fiction for engagement with neurotechnology.

Session Organizers:

Annie Duchesne, University of Northern British Columbia

Antye Guenther, Maastricht University

Anelis Kaiser Trujillo, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität

Freiburg, University College Freiburg

Flora Lysen, Maastricht University

Chair:

Sigrid Schmitz, HU Berlin

094. Rights of Nature: STS perspectives

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Participants:

Death of a Glacier and the Rights of Nature *Cymene Howe, Rice University*

In 2014, the first of Iceland's major glaciers, Okjökull, was lost to climate change. A relatively small glacier atop an extinct shield volcano, Ok had drawn little attention during its 700-year existence and yet its expiration, or “death,” clearly told a much larger story about climate change and human imprint. Five years later, during my anthropological research on Icelandic melt, Ok’s

story did get told, in part through my co-creation of the world's first memorial to a fallen glacier. The frameworks undergirding Rights of Nature tend to prioritize the right of ecosystems to regenerate, but in this case we find a signal of de-creation, degeneration or expiration. On one level, this paper reflects on the value of collective mourning in the face of climatological loss and explores what can be grievable—offering a challenge to scientific categories of “the living” and the non-living. (A glacier is not by scientific definition “alive,” even if it exhibits liveliness in its movements and in the glaciological designations of its corporeal parts: glacial “snouts,” “toes,” and “tongues.”) On another level, this paper proposes that mechanisms of legal personhood (and rights) are fortified when ceremonial and lively significance is attached to their subject. If rationalist science can be redefined when its epistemic values allow nature to be a rights-bearing subject, this paper asks how the contours of rationalist science may also be redefined through humanistic ceremonial forms held in honor of the non-human and the non-living.

Expertise and the knowledge politics of the Rights of Nature in Ecuador *Cristina Espinosa*

In 2008 Ecuador adopted a news-worthy constitution. Its preamble outlines the objective of promoting good relations, marked by diversity and harmony, between humans and nonhumans. Besides from individual and collective human rights, this constitution, for the first time in history, recognizes nature as a rights-holder. Such legal development has been key for social organizations and movements questioning the entrenchment of an extractive economy and demanding the preservation of socio-natural resources upon which suitable qualities of life and livelihoods depend. In this contribution, I focus on the emblematic case of Intag. Since the 1990s, this valley located in the Andean mountain range has witnessed a long-lasting socio-ecological conflict with fluctuating degrees of violence unfolding in connection to a large-scale copper mining project currently known as Llurimagua. Using a qualitative case-study methodology and building on academic discussions and concepts from the Social Studies of Science about lay-expertise relations, activism and science and from Political Ecology about knowledge politics, I examine the (counter-)knowledge forms and practices entangled in the process that lead to an unprecedented court ruling in favour of the Rights of Nature over the economic rights of the mining companies in September 2020. Furthermore, I discuss issues of representation and ‘voice’ of nonhuman entities and their links to science, society and democratic citizenship.

"Fish doesn't complain, plants don't complain!": Sociotechnical Imaginaries and the Environmental Reparation Process in the Rio Doce basin, in Minas Gerais/Brazil *Leonardo Guilherme Van Leeuwen, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS/Brasil); Lorena Fleury, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS)*

This paper analyzes the sociotechnical imaginaries present in the environmental reparation process of the Rio Doce basin, related to the rupture of the Fundão dam, in Minas Gerais/Brazil. On November 5th, 2015, the Fundão dam, owned by the company Samarco (Vale S.A. and BHP Billiton) breaks, creating one of the biggest sociotechnical disasters in the world. In March 2016, with the intention of leading and mediating the reparatory process, the Renova Foundation is created. In this context, this research sought to understand – based on the future imagined by Renova technicians – how science and technology produce and reorder nature and social life based on reparation. The study uses the coproductionist approach as theoretical starting point, as described by Jasanoff (2004), having as a main analytical concept the one of sociotechnical imaginaries developed by the same author and Sang-Hyun Kim (2009; 2015). The analysis were performed with data contained in documents, data collected

through interviews carried out with a group of technicians from Renova, as well as data that emerged through the observation process. It was possible to draw from the results that the imaginary that produces the repair is linked to the projection of a situation prior to the disaster; which aims to guide the reparatory actions and translate science as the main agent for the recovery of a world that has been destroyed. However, from the technicians involved it is possible to realize that the previous situation should not necessarily serve as an ideal for repair.

Science, Environment, and Sovereignty: Notions of Nature in Debates About Hawai'i's Observatories (1950s-present day) *Pascal Marichalar, CNRS/IRIS*

Since the 1950s, astronomers and other scientists have been building observatories on Hawai'i's tallest mountains. Scientific “site reports” justifying the telescopes’ construction described the sites as pristine, offering “pure” field science conditions in order to monitor the level of atmospheric CO₂ or to access the furthest reaches of the universe. “Environmental Impact Statements” and “Master Plans” defined natural resources worthy of conservation, and attempted to show that scientific activities could be carried out without encroaching on nature. Once the observatories were constructed, local environmental regulations were passed to ensure that the natural conditions remained optimal for science, through curbs on airborne pollution and on urban light pollution. Notions of nature have also played a central role in the resistance to astronomical development. As of the 1970s, environmental organizations such as the Hawaii Audubon Society and Sierra Club opposed the astronomical developments in the name of the conservation of rare fauna and flora. With the rebirth of the Hawaiian sovereignty movement in the 1970s, the language equating nature with traditional Hawaiian cultural practices, values and beliefs became more present. In the 2010s, the Flores-Case ‘ohana (family) brought a legal case against the construction of a new Thirty Meter Telescope at the summit of Mauna Kea, in which its members attempted (unsuccessfully) to get legal standing for Hawaiian deities linked to nature. This presentation is based on archives collected and analyzed since 2019; as well as ethnographic interviews and observations carried out on Hawai'i Island in 2020.

The Rights of Birds and the Politics of Mineral Extraction in Colombia *Angela Castillo, University of California at Berkeley*

This paper explores Central Colombia's birds' juridical and political lives amidst the legal and sociopolitical conflict created by the potential establishment of the La Colosa large-scale gold mining project. Drawing on ethnographic and archival research in Tolima, I analyze how birds entered the dispute through a local scientists-led monitoring initiative, which revealed a richer bird species diversity than the one reported by the mining company's 2008 EIA. Such initiative, which a group of local biologists carried out alongside anti-mining activists, allowed the enrollment of birds as fundamental subjects of anti-mining coalitions' practices of contestation (different forms of environmental litigation and initiatives to make Tolima a birdwatching landscape). In particular, I examine how the 2018 Tolima's District Court decision granting the Cocora River basin special rights and the 2021 Tolima State Assembly's decree proclaiming ten bird species as “highly-ecological important animals” conferred birds special legal protection. I show that the techno-scientific, legal, and political dynamics involved in the anti-mining coalition struggle against La Colosa created an ontology that rendered birds (i.e., their bodies, colors, movements, and sounds) as tangible and significant. I reflect on the challenges that this ontology presents for scientific production, environmental governance, and social movements’ activities in Tolima and Colombia. I argue that the focus on birds takes conversations on the rights of nature beyond the courtroom and decenters the role of the underground as the preferred site of inquiry to understand mining politics. Birds’ rights allow forests’

canopy, the skies, elevated electrical infrastructures to be the sites where the dynamics of mineral resource extraction are also lived and contested.

Session Organizer:

Javiera Barandiaran, University of California, Santa Barbara

095. Digital Inclusion In Practices - II: Increasing digital skills

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Accompanying cooperative digital practices and reciprocal exchanges of knowledge *Laurent Tessier, Institut Catholique de Paris*

Teachers training in digital pedagogy is a key issue for schools and universities. Due to the rise of these practices (such as hybrid or distance learning that have been intensively deployed in the context of the Covid19), educational institutions must now find ways to support teachers who have not yet mastered them. However, in this matter, classic teacher training methods often fail, especially when they do not focus on the participant's own discipline or research field (they can encounter sheer refusal of training, lack of confidence in the proposal or dropping out during training). All these issues are intensified by some kind of shame linked to digital illiteracy. In this paper, the authors propose to discuss three continuing education projects aimed at acquiring digital skills and based on cooperation and reciprocal exchanges of knowledge between teachers. Firstly, we will explore the creation of a digital pedagogy cooperative within their university; then, the design and broadcasting of a SPOC entitled "Digital Commons for Education"; and finally, the organizing of an event included in the "EdCamp" foundation's program. These three initiatives have one thing in common: they all reject the pedagogical approach of lecture training. On the contrary, they are based on the exchange of knowledge and know-how between practitioners. But we will also see that each of these three initiatives is based on a specific approach of coaching. Finally, we will see how each of them gives a slightly different place and form to the autonomous practices of participants.

Learning How to Go On: Becoming Digitally Literate in the Smart Home *Line Kryger Aagaard, Aalborg University Copenhagen; Kirsten Gram-Hanssen, Aalborg University Copenhagen; Toke Haunstrup Christensen, Aalborg University Copenhagen*

Smart home technology is expected to be widespread in the future and might accommodate a green transition by making energy consumption and production meet better, but it may also have social consequences, which are important to understand. At a basic level, we need to know more about how it is to learn to live with these technologies, and how they influence our everyday practices and routines. This paper is based on autoethnography, a two-year diary of one of the authors, and it uses theories of practice in investigating to what extent learning to live with new smart technologies are different from learning to live with other types of new materiality. Theories of learning have a well-established tradition within theories of practice and include the collectivity of learning processes. The concept of "knowing how to go on" is central in some of this work. Smart home technologies are appropriated within the context of the private home, and learning processes are thus done alone or collectively within the household. This raises new questions of how to understand the collectivity in learning processes. This paper will utilize in-depth autoethnographic knowledge to gain insight into the adoption of new smart home technologies and how these interact with learning processes and the establishing of new everyday practices. Such an approach can lay the ground for further empirical work with a broader empirical material and provide knowledge that can help in designing better technologies

and make policy and regulation promote this.

Minors and digital offenses *Emilie Potin, Rennes 2 University; Gaël Henaff, Rennes 2 University*

Authors and / or victims, the minors are involved in transgressions that take place in the social digital space. Juvenile delinquency can be seen on digital systems and networks, as a target for a violation of the law (illegal system interference, illegal data interference...) or as a means to commit one (trolling, counterfeiting, child pornography...) (Benbouzid and Ventre 2016). Behind the screens, offenders are able to exploit their anonymity to commit offenses with relative impunity. Whether it is the characterization of digital offences or digital educational support, juvenile justice faces constant technological transformations and juvenile digital behaviours that call for change. In the specific scope of the PJJ's intervention, how far does the area of offenses extend? Who are the young offenders? What are the type of issues related to judicial intervention on these digital devices? From a socio-legal approach, this proposition aims to understand how social media influences juvenile criminal justice and how the latter copes with it. The research aims to develop elements of knowledge and analysis that link digital behaviours (Pasquier 2020), juvenile deviance (Becker 1985) and the related educational and legal responses (Chantraine and Sallée 2013; Coutant 2005; Faget 2009). Gathering a quantitative approach and an ethnographic perspective in France, the survey will take an inventory of practices while situating them in specific configurations.

Session Organizer:

Céline Borelle, SENSE - Orange labs / CEMS - CNRS

Chair:

Valérie Peugeot, SENSE - Orange labs

Discussant:

Céline Borelle, SENSE - Orange labs / CEMS - CNRS

096. Food for care: Interrogating practices of eating in troubled worlds - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

How care manifests (or not) in everyday encounters with food and practices of eating in? How to nourish relations of care while nourishing the bodies? Studies from STS, food anthropology, and sociology present a variety of accounts of food-induced socialities and socio-material relations (production challenges, security and environmental change, boundaries between the eater and the eaten, digitalisation and platformization of food, etc). This panel attends to the mundane and everyday instances of relating to, with and through eating. Mundane encounters with food manifest social class, gendered work division, colonial attitudes, socio-economic inequalities, and the moral balance between health and pleasure. Responsibilization of eating and cooking transforms the kitchen and the dining table into a boundary terrain for public health campaigns, environmental concerns, and hedonistic searches for pleasure. This panel asks what is or can be neglected as we care for what and how we eat? Especially as sanitary regimes of lockdowns, confinements, and curfews forefront eating in and intensify invisible work. We invite multidisciplinary works which tackle eating as a learned, trained, proceduralized, and performed practice shaping relations to science, governance, health, pleasure, solidarity, and care. We welcome attention to the embodied aspect of eating and cooking, including interactions with products, elements, instruments, and technology. Following food studies scholars, submissions may be analytically focused on three points and their interrelations: social occasions, food selections, and processes of body incorporation. Finally, we are curious about methodological and speculative reflections on the transformative side of research into the practices of eating. This session is the second session of the panel subtitled "Food practices in context: New divides and invisible labor during COVID 19 pandemics"

Participants:

Purifying the Body (Politic): Clean Eating, Racialised

Pseudoscience and Sinophobia *Kerry Mackereth, University of Cambridge*

The rise of the 'clean eating' movement has generated considerable public debate, including critiques of the (pseudo-)scientific basis of the claims made by clean eating advocates and influencers; the relationship between clean eating and disordered eating; and the whiteness of the clean eating space (Tandoh 2017; Warner 2017; Wilson 2017; Pandika 2020; O'Neill 2020a, 2020b). While there is some scholarship that examines the relative exclusion of people of colour from the clean eating industry and how people of colour in the wellness industry negotiate this space (O'Neill 2020b), this paper pushes forward scholarship on gender, racialisation and clean eating by examining clean eating's relationship with scientific racism and racialised (pseudo-)science. It focuses on how discourses of bodily purity shape the clean eating movement, focusing on the coding of 'toxic foods' as foreign substances that invade and sully the purity of both the individual body and the wider body politic. This presentation then takes as its specific example the racialisation and stigmatisation of Chinese food in the clean eating movement, examining how its marginalisation plays into the clean eating movement's politics of whiteness. To this end, this paper then explores the connection between clean eating and anti-vaccination movements in the context of the global COVID-19 pandemic, arguing that these overlapping movements are both premised on the notion of protecting the white, female body from penetration and invasion by external pathogens. Hence, it concludes that clean eating invokes pernicious racialising discourses beyond its more overt aesthetics of whiteness.

Coping Through Comfort Food: An Anthropological Investigation Of Health, Wellbeing, And Eating In Oaxaca, Mexico *Kayla Hurd, University of Notre Dame*

Coping mechanisms help people who have been displaced from their homes during crises, but what happens when the displacement is social, and people are forced to shift inside their homes? The COVID-19 pandemic presents itself as a novel opportunity to examine how people cope with this sudden shift into their homes and its impact on their choices about health and wellbeing. Specifically, I investigate how people use food as a coping mechanism to the COVID-19 pandemic despite structural barriers that are limiting food access/choice. Building upon pilot data from participants in Oaxaca, Mexico, who claimed to be choosing healthier foods despite the pandemic's structural and social barriers, I explore questions of the mundane as I ask about people's perceptions of their diet before and after the pandemic and biologically examine the embodiment of these choices. This project aims to examine if people have acquired new habits and perceptions about food and the impact these new choices may have on their bodies. Using methods in cultural (ethnography, free lists/pile sorts, interviews, questionnaires) and biological (nutritional analysis, bodily measurements) anthropology, I explore the concept of care through coping practices concerning food selection and how this nourishes people's bodies in low-income communities. I use a critical biocultural perspective to further understand how people rethink their behavior and operationalize how people build resilience to social and structural barriers through their food choices.

Caring for Food and Food for Care: Transformations in Foodways Amidst COVID-19 Lockdowns in Malaysia *Elise Mognard, Taylor's University; Anindita Dasgupta, Taylor's University*

Malaysia is a multi-cultural and multi-religious Southeast Asian society undergoing rapid urbanization and industrialization. Since mid-March 2020, the Movement Control Order has been declared to curb the Covid-19 pandemic. This study attempts to go beyond the initial disruptions of routines in everyday life, by focusing on structural transformations in food patterns taking shape in the wider process of compressed modernization. With

diverse degrees of restrictions in the movements, eateries and business operations, this period is investigated to study strategies used by Malaysians to alleviate movement restrictions in food homemaking. We ask which social and cultural norms and practices related to foodways - and their gendered division - are emerging within Malaysian society during the lockdowns. The empirical material for this study is drawn from reflective interviews with Malaysian professionals from the three main ethnic groups in peninsular Malaysian metropolises. Exploratory fieldwork has unveiled how the lockdowns - and their subsequent 'work from home' - has led to renegotiation of the division of the socio-cultural and invisible food related work at home and subsequent learning of embodied skills in selecting and cooking food by ones. Additionally, relations of care and solidarity are asserted by sourcing or cooking for neighbours, friends or relatives while ambivalent connections between (re)appropriation and normative injunction of food production and preparation, as well as between pleasure of food and body image consciousness are emerging amidst this troubled and yet now mundane experiences of Malaysians.

Locked-Down Labour: Representation of Women in Kerala Food Vlogs *Vanya Rachel Gnaniah, University of Waterloo*

This paper will analyse how the labour of women in the preparation of food is central to the construction of identity. In order to explore this, I look specifically at the State of Kerala in India whose unique history of trade, climate and landscape has enabled food to function as a central marker of Malayalee (a person from Kerala) identity. I will engage in a close analysis of videos uploaded by popular YouTube vloggers from the State of Kerala focusing specifically on the videos uploaded during the March 2020 lockdown. Unlike the other provinces in India, the lockdown was strictly enforced by the local government thereby preventing the possibility for vloggers to visit restaurants and other kitchens. This caused them to turn their attention to the home. Consequently, the work of women in these households were highlighted which indicated the crucial way in which women knit together the past with the present in the minute choices that they make in the process of food preparation. Additionally, the visual representation and the narrative of "mother's cooking" or "wife's cooking" by male vloggers become central to their affirmation of their identity as "Malayalee" (a person from Kerala). Therefore, the procurement of material for food and the employment of various methods of preparation enables a unique binding together of history and local landscape which is primarily accomplished by women.

Session Organizer:

Alexandra Endaltseva, CNRS - CERTOP

Chair:

Anne Dupuy Hoang, Université de Toulouse Jean Jaurès/
CERTOP UMR-CNRS 5044

Discussant:

Jean-Pierre Poulain, Université de Toulouse Jean Jaurès/
CERTOP UMR-CNRS 5044

097. STS Labs Otherwise

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Science and Technology Studies has long had an interest in studying laboratories and how they construct knowledge and do politics in seemingly mundane day-to-day practices. More recently, STSers and others have taken up the laboratory model to do research in ways that address the politics of knowledge production, professionalization, funding, ethics, and authorship, among other topics. This roundtable brings together the leaders of a diverse set of laboratory spaces that explicitly address power structures at the everyday level of operating a research space. Topics for discussion will include funding, management, authorship and membership, reading, and other professionalization and research relationships. Overall, we aim to show how lab directors are creating spaces to do research

"otherwise." [Scheduling: this should be a double-size roundtable!]

Presenters:

Michelle Murphy, University of Toronto
Nicholas Shapiro, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)
Emilia Sanabria, CNRS - CERMES3
Beth Coleman, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto
Kristen Bos, University of Toronto
Tao Leigh Goffe, Cornell University
Jeffrey Palmer, Cornell University
Eve Tuck, University of Toronto
Max Liboiron, Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador
Joseph Dumit, UC Davis

Session Organizers:

Joseph Dumit, UC Davis
Max Liboiron, Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador

Chairs:

Max Liboiron, Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador
Joseph Dumit, UC Davis

098. Forensic Devices: How They Mediate, How They Are Discussed, How They Mitigate Interprofessional Conflicts - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

The term “forensics” derives from the Latin word “forensis” meaning “belonging to the forum, market (place)”. The etymology recalls that court proceedings and investigations are public affairs and so they were often conducted on the Forum in ancient Rome. Following this line of thought, several STS works have depicted how experts present forensic findings in the courtroom, explain their evidence and put them up for evaluation. Recent papers have then turned to the epistemic foundations of forensic science. In our panel we want to take up these discussions and push them in a new direction. For while the relationship between forensics and law is already well studied, the intersections of forensics and the society/public, forensics and basic science, and forensics and the police have hardly been explored so far. We propose to take a closer look at these relations by using the example of forensic devices. By forensic devices we do not only mean machines and tools, but also databases, information technologies, and procedures guiding forensic practices. We are looking for studies dedicated to the social life of forensic devices, to their role as mediators or boundary objects between different areas and fields of practice, as well as the public debate about their trustworthiness, risks and chances. We particularly encourage contributions focussing on how these devices help their users to navigate the gap between – and the quest for loyalty to – the realm of investigation on the one hand and the realm of science on the other.

Participants:

Building a Postcolonial Carceral State: South Africa's Forensic DNA Database *Noah Tamarkin, Cornell University*

This paper considers links between South Africa's biometric histories (Breckenridge 2014) and one manifestation of South African biometrics in the present: a national forensic DNA database that was established in 2015 when legislation was passed that regulated its scope and formalized the role of the South African Police Service (SAPS) in its expansion and maintenance. As a decolonizing state, postapartheid South Africa was actively engaged in dismantling apartheid policing when they pivoted to a renewed focus on state carcerality via forensic science. I'm interested in teasing out historical linkages as one way to account for this pivot. Taking the DNA database as a forensic device, this paper asks how forensic genetics mediates dual postcolonial concerns: divesting from colonially-inherited forms of oppression and investing in popularly circulating demands for safety and security. Mediation is especially pertinent

here given that forensic genetics can recapitulate aspects of these colonial forms. I argue that debates about the specific regulations that will govern South Africa's national DNA database ultimately worked to obscure colonial continuities, thus depoliticizing forensic genetics such that it could be endorsed by a wide range of South Africans differently situated in colonial and apartheid histories.

In the Name of Peace: Coexisting Forensic Practices ss Transitional Justice Devices. The Case of The Colombian (Post) Conflict. *Maria Fernanda Olarte-Sierra, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research, University of Amsterdam*

Colombia has endured a long-lasting armed conflict since the 1960s that has produced over 9.000.000 country-wide. In this context, forensic experts have played a fundamental role in identifying the victims. As a result of the peace agreement signed between the now-extinct guerrilla group FARC-EP and the Colombian government in 2016, two forensic teams were established as part of the governmental agencies created to ensure the agreement's implementation. One group is the forensic experts that are part of the Special Jurisdiction for Peace, which is the transitional justice tribunal. The other belongs to the Unit for the Search of the Disappeared, a humanitarian and extrajudicial unit, which aims to contribute to the reparation of victims and their right to truth. Each forensic team is to deal differently with the aftermath of the armed conflict. Regardless of their differences, these teams are to work collaboratively to facilitate peace and reconciliation. Thus, although they may work coordinately at times, at others, they may be in tension or interact non-coherently. In this talk, I will address how these two newly created sets of forensic teams may act as mediators of the right to truth and reparation for victims while serving, also as devices for accessing transitional justice benefits for known perpetrators. Attending to these closely related but differentiated forensic practices helps to come closer to the broader social effects of forensic work amidst and armed conflict and understand how the wider public is involved in the logic of forensic practices.

Post-mortem Imaging in the Forensic Device: Practices of Seeing and Interprofessional Debates *Celine Schnegg, Haute Ecole de Sante Vaud; Séverine Rey, Haute école de santé Vaud HES-SO; Alejandro Dominguez, Haute Ecole de Sante Vaud*

Modern post-mortem imaging – post-mortem computed tomography, post-mortem magnetic resonance imaging, post-mortem computed tomographic angiography and 3D Surface Scanning or photogrammetry – is increasingly used as a complement to conventional autopsy. As an innovation often considered revolutionary, it allows to see inside the body without “cutting” it. Noninvasive, it enables to “mimic” the living while the bodies are perfused, ventilated and digitally reconstructed. Indeed, angiography artificially restores blood circulation and makes it possible to visualize the vascular system in an unprecedented way. On the basis of an ethnographic research in a Swiss forensic medicine department developing, promoting and using post-mortem imaging, we discuss the post-mortem imaging integration in the forensic daily practices. Despite the attested added diagnostic value of post-mortem imaging in the scientific literature, these new “practices of seeing” (Goodwin, 2000) dead bodies give rise to debates between forensic pathologists, radiologists and radiographers. If organizational tensions arise due to the cohabitation of research and investigation priorities, main discussions concern the proximity degree and relationship between “virtual” and “real” bodies, as well as the probative value of post-mortem imaging, especially in cases of discordance between radiological and autopsy results. Following other ethnographic studies on forensic practices (Juston, 2020; Timmermans, 2006), our analysis combines a range of approaches in STS with a view taking into account the

visualization techniques (Burri et al., 2008; Golan, 2004; Reed et al., 2016), the ontology of bodies (Cussins, 1996; Mol, 2002), and the construction of expert judgment (Cole, 1998; Dodier, 1994; Lynch, 1998). References Burri, R.V., Dumit, J. 2008. "Social Studies of Scientific Imaging and Visualization", in E.J. Hackett, O. Amsterdamska, M. Lynch & J. Wajcman (Eds), *The Handbook of Science and Technology Studies* (pp. 297-317). Cambridge: MIT Press. Cole, S.A. 1998. "Witnessing Identification: Latent Fingerprinting Evidence and Expert Knowledge". *Social Studies of Science*, 28(5-6): 687-712. Cussins, C. 1996. "Ontological Choreography: Agency through Objectification in Infertility Clinics". *Social Studies of Science*, 26(3): 575-610. Dodier, N. 1994. "Expert Medical Decisions in Occupational Medicine: A Sociological Analysis of Medical Judgement". *Sociology of Health and Illness*, 16(4): 489-514. Golan, T. 2004. "The Emergence of the Silent Witness: The Legal and Medical Reception of X-rays in the USA". *Social Studies of Science*, 34(4): 469-499. Goodwin, C. 2000. "Practices of Seeing. Visual Analysis: An Ethnomethodological Approach", in T. van Leeuwen & C. Jewitt (Eds), *Handbook of Visual Analysis* (pp. 157-182). London: SAGE. Juston Morival, R. 2020. *Médecins légistes. Une enquête sociologique*. Paris: Les Presses de Sciences Po. Lynch, M. 1998. "The Discursive Production of Uncertainty: The OJ Simpson 'Dream Team' and the Sociology of Knowledge Machine". *Social Studies of Science*, 28(5-6): 829-868. Mol, A. 2002. *The Body Multiple: Ontology in Medical Practice*. Durham, N.C.: Duke University Press. Reed, K., Kochetkova, I., Molyneux-Hodgson, S. 2016. "'You're looking for different parts in a jigsaw': fetal MRI (magnetic resonance imaging) as an emerging technology in professional practice". *Sociology of Health & Illness*, 38(5): 736-752. Timmermans, S. 2006. *Postmortem: How Medical Examiners Explain Suspicious Deaths*. Chicago: University of Chicago Press.

Session Organizer:

Veronika Lipphardt, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, University College Freiburg

Chair:

Nils Ellebrecht, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

099. Scaling the Ethical Plateaus of Energy Justice - I

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Energy systems are in a state of flux. Climate change, the COVID-19 pandemic, the collapse of oil and destabilized energy economies have forced the world's energopolitical regimes (Boyer 2019) to grapple with new and evolving demands on and for energy infrastructures. These geopolitical shifts signal both emerging windows of opportunity and causes for concern, as the ethical plateaus that have come to define contemporary energy ecologies rupture at their fault lines. The growing set of diverse conceptual complements with which energy is often paired (e.g., energy rights, energy vulnerability, energy democracy, energy transitions, etc.) betray different assumptions about the scales and systems of relevance to energy politics and to processes of sociotechnical change. Energy justice, by contrast, calls for a more holistic view of the ethics informed by unique energy ecologies—i.e. the historically and culturally specific modes of relating to one's self, to other humans, to non-human life, and to the environment through one's relationship to energy and energy infrastructures. This means that more nuanced attention is needed to account for and enact just energy relations in situ. Session #1 "Framing Energy Justice" includes empirical and theoretical papers that critique, reconstruct, or provide alternative framings of energy justice.

Participants:

Interspecies Energy Justice: Bringing the Nonhuman World into the Energy Transition Debate *Giovanni Frigo*, *Institute for Technology Assessment and Systems Analysis (ITAS)*, *Karlsruhe Institute of Technology* (; *Christine Milchram*,

ITAS/KIT

Developing a moral concern for the nonhuman world has been the crux of many scholars in environmental ethics. In the field of environmental justice (EJ), some authors have proposed to move beyond anthropocentric views by considering the well-being of animals and plants, and even of entire ecosystems (e.g. Plumwood 2002). The terms interspecies justice appropriately captures the attempt to extend moral considerability to those beings and entities that are other-than-human. Rather surprisingly, however, such reflections have remained within the EJ scholarship and failed to influence the emerging field of energy justice (EneJ), that is a key component of the energy transition. In this paper, I contend that by being mostly preoccupied with the goal of "humanizing the sociotechnical transition" (Jenkins et al. 2018), EneJ remains fundamentally anthropocentric and therefore shortsighted in light of the ecological dimensions of the energy transition. In fact, the expansion and modification of energy systems does not affect only human lives but also the well-being of non-human beings and ecosystems. Given that energy transition, global climate change, resources scarcity and biodiversity loss are in many ways intertwined issues which particularly affect the Global South, I argue that interspecies justice should be brought into the discussion about the energy transition. This theoretical update can lead to radical changes in the ways public policy is envisioned, intersectionality is thought, and activism is justified and carried out.

Questioning the Right to Services: How Energy System Enigma Frustrates Socially Just Imaginaries *Alison Kenner*, *Drexel University*

Energy rights discourse has emerged in new forms in response to COVID-19 vulnerabilities. Adjacent to the tenants rights movement, advocacy for a right to energy presents a different set of challenges due to the complexity of energy supply systems, as well as the politics of carbon-reductions. Yet within the context of growing household energy vulnerability -- a trend only increased by the pandemic -- questions about equity, access, and affordability are salient, particularly as the gap between efficiency technologies and aging housing stock widens, for example, and climate change exacerbates risk. What possibilities do rights discourse afford in relation to energy services; do "rights" place too much emphasis on supply rather than demand; and how do rights interface with energy justice, as a move towards more equitable and sustainable societies? This paper draws on data from ethnographic interviews conducted with more than 200 people living in the U.S. Mid-Atlantic region; interview data is situated in relation to longstanding federal energy assistance policy designed specifically to address utility insecurity. Discussion exposed tension between the impossibility of surviving (let alone succeeding) in society without contemporary energy services, and the sense of obligation that one should pay for energy -- particularly in the context of environmental protection. Drawing on the work of feminist political theorists, this paper argues that rights discourse is present as a minoritarian formation in policy arenas, and among household energy users, but that both policy and everyday imaginaries are frustrated by the enigma of energy systems.

Recognizing justice in energy storage: revising the concept of recognition justice *Nynke van Uffelen*, *TU Delft*

Due to the intermittency of renewable energy sources, the transition to a low-carbon economy highly depends on energy storage. The energy transition must be just, stressing the importance of protecting vulnerable groups from injustice. In the field of energy research, energy justice is often divided in three tenets: distributional justice, procedural justice and recognition justice. As part of my PhD research which started in January 2021 I will focus on the third tenet of justice. The richer and more inclusive our concept of recognition, the higher the chances

of more and better recognition for groups or individuals that are somehow misrecognized. Currently, the often-used conceptions of recognition justice appear to be too narrow in three dimensions: recognition justice and procedural justice are conceptually blended into one; it is mainly used in a descriptive and explanatory way; and it is seen as a means to an end. Given the three dimensions where mainstream conceptions of recognition justice can be amended, I see three ways in order to enrich the definition by going back to the roots of the concept in critical theory and looking at recognition philosophers Nancy Fraser and Axel Honneth. I will provide a revised concept of recognition justice that provides a better and more inclusive tool in our search for misrecognition and injustices in the real world. I will discuss the application of these insights by discussing misrecognition in the case of hydrogen storage technologies.

Reinventing Energy Ethics *Jacob Bethem*

While authors are answering calls to acknowledge the importance of ethical issues related to energy decisions, energy research lacks a structured approach for evaluating ethical decisions. Without a guiding framework, articles written on energy ethics appear as merely opinionated or noncontroversial. It is uncommon for authors who write about energy ethics to use the term 'energy ethics' or to explicitly use philosophical principles to support their claims. Current definitions of energy ethics obscure whether this research is meant to be descriptive or critical, and while some authors have integrated ethical theory, their frameworks significantly differ or are less comprehensive than conventional views. In response, I reinvent energy ethics as the analysis of questions of right and wrong using a framework for prescribing actions and proper policies within private and public energy decisions. Redefined as a distinct subdiscipline of applied ethics, applied energy ethics can help to unite this young, growing field of research and introduce academic rigor to ethical evaluations so as to provide greater support to energy decision-making. I distinguish energy ethics from morality, justice, anthropology, metaphysics, and clarify other misconceptions in the field.

Rhetoric of/as Energy: An Ecological-Rhetorical Approach to Local Infrastructures *Ian Ferris, The University of Texas at Austin; Hannah Hopkins, University of Texas at Austin*

Conversations around networked technologies demand sustained engagement with the ethical dimensions of digital tools and their attendant infrastructures. The mechanisms that make our datafied lives possible are bound up in petrocapiatist exploitation: assemblages of digital technologies visit harm on marginalized communities, and the growing energy demands and massive ecological tolls of those assemblages are increasingly destructive and, by design, invisibilized. The ethical complexities of such energy ecologies call for nascent perspectives in ecologically-oriented rhetorical scholarship that grapple with the embodied, more-than-human, and interconnected entanglements that comprise rhetoricity. In particular, there is growing interest in a reorientation to rhetoric itself as energy, for example in what Druschke calls a "trophic rhetoric" in which the rhetorician attunes to flows of polyvalent energies that hold members of rhetorical ecologies in relation. Grounded in analysis of local energy ecologies in our community in Austin, Texas, we attend to these human and more-than human entanglements. In approaching material infrastructures in a way that more clearly surfaces data cultures' labor and ecological exploitation, we turn to energy justice. Engaging an ecological-rhetorical approach in service of scaling the ethical plateaus of energy justice means attuning simultaneously to the rhetoric of energy and rhetoric as energy, yielding fruitful insights both for the panel at hand as well as for ongoing conversations in ecological rhetorics.

Session Organizer:

James Adams, University of California, Irvine

100. Science, Technology and Innovation Policy in non-

hegemonic countries: emulation, adaptation, creation

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Participants:

Big Data Economies: Translation and How "Data" Makes Canada and Africa *Anna M. Agathangelou, York University; Mishall Ahmed, York University, Canada*

Big data is the emerging field where innovative technology offers new ways to extract value from available information. The idea of translation is central to "big data" - from government censuses to financial markets, to everyday digital transactions and interactions- and its organization in making particular ways of knowing and governing populations. As policymakers, researchers, financial traders pin the possibility of profits and innovation on such information I want to trace how different actors politically mobilize and translate data along with and against official, data-driven, cost-benefit calculations about finances (Jasanoff, 2017). Translation, that is, conveying, moving, or transforming of coordinates in which the new axes are parallel to the old ones, stresses the entanglements of scientifically known bodies such as finance, informatics and now big data. In this paper, we use two major reports produced by the Chamber of Commerce in Canada Data Fast Forward: A Prescription for Innovation, Balance and Trust (2019), A Data Deficit: The Risk of Getting It Wrong (December 2018), and a third report produced by the Brookings Institution Harnessing Africa's Digital Potential: New Tools for a New Age (2018) to show how Canada and Africa are now assembling and translating different kinds of data and methods to co-produce themselves as powerful states with subjects of innovation. We will show that big data assemblage and its translation co-produces notions of innovation along with sovereign dominant states and subjects that are "left behind." The big data field is, thus, a rich site of co-production and its analysis.

Is it Possible to Socialize a Science and Technology Park? The case of Polish cities *Jacek Gadecki, University of Science and Technology AGH; Lukasz Afeltowicz, AGH University of Science and Technology; Karolina Anielska, Jagiellonian University, Institute of Geography and Spatial Management; Ilona Morawska, Institute of Urban and Regional Development*

Poland is an example of a non-hegemonic country that has followed the path of imitation of innovation policy. An example of imitation was building numerous science and technology parks. They were created at a time when hegemonic states were departing from them. Dozens of parks have been built, many of which have not survived the test of time. The remaining parks exist in isolated locations where interaction with business and science is difficult. The very space of parks itself favours the isolation of companies and creative individuals. All this hinders knowledge spillovers, risk sharing, competence coupling and other processes that economic geography recognizes as important factors favouring innovation. However, most authorities, park staff and experts are well aware of this. And attempts are made to socialize parks. They try to integrate the tenants' community. Some parks host various events integrating people from innovative industries. They also try to support innovative activities outside their walls. We devote our presentation to attempts to socialize a science and technology park in Kraków, one of the biggest Polish cities. We also present the results of anthropological and geographic research conducted by us in three other large Polish cities. This study shows a number of measures that compensate for the city's policies and poor design of the parks. It also shows the tensions arising from attempts to integrate parks into an innovative environment.

Kerala Model of Innovation? Entrepreneurial Understandings of Innovation in a Southern Indian State *Aalok Khandekar,*

Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad; Mohammed Raqib, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad

The southern Indian state of Kerala presents a unique context from which to examine the adaptation, contestation, and transformation of innovation policies. On the one hand, Kerala has often been hailed as exemplary in terms of its achievements in healthcare provision and education even under relatively low-resource conditions (popularly referred to as the “Kerala Model [of development]”), owing to successive communist and socialist governments in the state since Indian independence. On the other hand, this has also resulted in low levels of industrialisation in the state and a heavy dependence of its economy on remittances from its overseas citizens (often based in Gulf countries). It is against this backdrop that we examine the Kerala’s recent foray into cultivating entrepreneurial activity in the state in its attempts to benefit from immersing itself in the knowledge economy. In particular, we focus on how entrepreneurs within Kerala’s start-up ecosystem themselves perceive the need for “innovation.” Drawing on data collected through ethnographic interviews, participant observation, and media and documentary analysis, we demonstrate the particular ways in which global discourses of innovation get localized: Kerala’s tech-entrepreneurs seem to selectively draw on various discursive resources at different scales (local, regional, national, and transnational) in order to explain what innovation means to them in the context of Kerala. In conformity with this panel’s theme, we thus demonstrate how Kerala’s techno-entrepreneurial ecosystem, despite the global economic and business models at play, continues to also harbour unique, non-confirmative and localized understandings of innovation.

Living and Working Science Policies: The Case of Latvia *Jeva Puzo, Riga Stradins University*

The paper aims to investigate the recent science policies in Latvia from the perspective of research workers. In recent years, Latvia’s science policies, as well as well as other policies envisioning Latvia’s future path, posit “international cooperation” and “international competitiveness” in science at their core. At the same time, the number of international researchers in the country remains low. This intervention, through an examination of the experiences of international researchers in Latvia and their local counterparts from the perspective of interpretive and infrastructural labor, illuminates as to why that may be the case. It brings to the fore the toll it takes on research workers to fill the gaps and ruptures of science policies and research infrastructures. In the paper, I rely on the ethnographic data collected in Latvia in 2020 and 2021. During this time, I conducted semi-structured interviews, both in person and online, with researchers and administrators at Latvian research institutions, as well as government officials and bureaucrats overseeing the implementation of Latvia’s science policies. The interview data is supplemented by data collected through observation and participant observation in various online settings, as well as analysis of legislative materials and news sources. In line with the literature on the inequalities, insecurities and uncertainties embedded in the contemporary knowledge regimes across the globe, this paper contributes to STS by suggesting that, even though the amount and consequences of infrastructural and interpretive work performed by researchers increase, this labor remains undervalued by research performance indicators.

Scientific and technological development in Paraguay: pressures, adaptations and results of STIP in adverse contexts *Camilo Jose Caballero Ocariz, Universidad de Buenos Aires*

The set of elements that converge in the process of institutionalization of science in the Paraguayan State in the period 1989-2019 will be analyzed. More precisely, the relationship between the State and the actors who have an interest

in the national science and technology system is studied. Through the study of the normative frameworks, institutional designs, results and interviews with key actors, the focus will be placed on the way in which the State and the involved actors processed their interests and concepts on STIP, which led to the creation and first definitions of the National Council of Science and Technology in 1997. Also, the implementation of two stages of scientific policy instruments until 2019, with two different sources of funding markedly different. During this period, priorities, definitions of science, and the ways of evaluating the competitive funds for the various instruments changed. The Paraguayan case would present common issues and also particularities in relation to the process of the other countries of the region. Paraguay struggles stoically to find a place in a globalized but centralized world at the same time as seeking sustainability in its scientific and technological development. Visions that range from being efficiently inserted into the global distribution of science to developing some local paradigm of scientific development are debated in the future of science in Paraguay, conditioned by sectarian interests and political vicissitudes, however, there are learning experiences for reflection.

Sectoral Funds In Argentina. Mismatch Between Policy’s Assumptions And Local Environment. The Case Of Microelectronics. *Fernanda Andrea Soca, CONICET Universidad Nacional de Quilmes; Mariana Eva Di Bello, CONICET - UNQ- UNLP*

Sectoral Funds were conceived in Argentina as the emblematic instrument of what was called a "new generation of policies" aimed at strengthening relations between the scientific and the productive sector. From its implementation in 2010, various associative projects were supported in sectors and technologies identified as strategic. The tendency towards supporting specific capacities as well as public private partnership was so significant at the time that guided planning experience Plan Argentina Innovadora 2020. Based on an empirical case study on the call in ICT for 2010 -related to a public-private consortium in microelectronics-, we argue Sectoral Funds assumed the existence of a dynamic productive sector that demands innovative knowledge. It is stressed there is a disconnection between the assumptions underpinning the policy and the characteristics of the local environment in which the policy is implemented. Although the funding for associative projects was significantly higher than usual, this disconnection hinders the expected results to be achieved. We infer that this is not due to policy maker’s lack of knowledge -regarding the motivations and possibilities of local companies to engage in cooperation activities with the scientific sector- but to the stiffness of STIP, given by a shared understanding of how this cooperation should be carried out in the “world society” (Meyer, 2010). Our empirical findings show that the initiative to cooperate came from the scientific sector and that there was no significant set of companies that demanded the capabilities that were supported in the call in ICT of the year 2010.

Session Organizer:

Noela Invernizzi, Universidade Federal do Parana

101. Practicing Process Ontology in and with Biological Research – II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Biomedical fields increasingly understand life not as genetically determined, but as developing in relation to socio-material experiences. STS has discussed this development as the emergence of a postgenomic era or the biosocial turn, exploring how it changes views on genetics, bodies, their temporality and relationship to environments. For instance, engagements with environmental epigenetics, the microbiome, or viruses, reorient attention towards conceptualising phenomena, such as environment or disease, as relational entities across time and space.

Thinking with relationality is an approach we can also find in the philosophy of biology. Dupré (2018, 2020) and others further the notion of process ontology; a theory, which understands biological phenomena as constantly stabilising processes with and in their environments instead of closed entities. While we can observe attempts of biologists themselves to address life as processual in research designs (e.g., applying a life-course perspective), we seek to make a shift in the ontological status of biological thinking more explicit: how does biology come from theory to practice and vice versa? This panel aims to further discussions on process ontology in STS and to consider how an interdisciplinary processual research agenda could look like in method and practice (Niewöhner/Lock 2018). We invite theoretical works that discuss how process ontology might inform biological theory as well as empirical engagements on how it becomes known experimentally and with what effects for understanding life. We also encourage ethnographic stories that make good relations visible (e.g., symbiotic relationships), contrasting prevailing reductionist accounts on health and disease in biology.

Participants:

Placental Relations Refigured: Thinking with Process in Epigenetic Research on Toxicants *Sophia Rossmann, MCTS, Technical University of Munich*

This talk engages with the question of what might unfold if we approach contemporary biomedical research from a process ontological perspective (Dupré, 2020; Dupré & Nicholson, 2018). Taking epigenetic research in environmental toxicology as a case study, how might foregrounding processual relations between environments and bodies, instead of understanding them as distinct entities, provide a more generative way to capture life in toxic worlds without proposing a new biological truism? Environmental epigenetics is a research approach from molecular biology that explores how environments, such as toxicants, induce biochemical and structural changes of DNA molecules that impact gene expression. In contrast to genetic mutations, these changes are not fixed but allow to understand bodies in constant becoming with the situated ecologies in which they dwell. Zooming in on ethnographic fieldwork in two research groups, I trace how environmental toxicologists conducting epigenetic research increasingly turn to the placenta as a promising epistemic object to make complex toxic relations visible. Here, the placenta is frequently referred to as a “mediator” between foetus, mother and outside worlds. However, scientific findings on how the placenta copes with toxicity by changing epigenetic regulation and thus its function might actually challenge the notion of a mediator. Rather, as I will show, the placenta in epigenetic research appears to be less a discrete object mediating between mother and foetus but rather emerges as a temporarily stabilised process that actively responds to and becomes with the toxicants it is exposed to.

Conceptualizing (Good) Relations with the Microbiome *Jane Dryden, Mount Allison University*

In response to developing scientific research about the human microbiome, particularly the gut microbiome, scholars across a range of fields have called for a shift in the way that people conceive of microbes. We have calls for a consideration of microbiomes as companion species (Beck 2021), an “affirmative microbiopolitics” (Ironstone 2019), and for exploring how the public can develop “a feeling for the microbiome” (Greenhough et al 2018). These calls evince enthusiasm for finding new ways of thinking of our selves as at least in part constituted through our relations with microbiome. In order to conceptualize what this might mean, scholars have explored what metaphors might be most useful, whether for the purpose of biology and clinical treatments (Morar and Bohannon 2019) or for the purpose of public health and communication (Baty et al 2014). This paper is interested in how this discourse gets taken up with respect to health, given the widespread paradigm of “personal responsibility for health” (Nettleton 1996) – specifically, how the deployment of these metaphors can then contribute to reinforcing

the idea that we ought to maintain a level of control over our health. In exploring this theme, the paper will draw on critiques of the ideology of cure, as developed by Disability Studies scholars such as Eli Clare (2017), to challenge the expectation of control. The paper argues for making space for messiness in the context of our relations with our microbiome.

Of Relationality in Human-Microbial Food Cultures *Sandra Widmer, York University, Canada*

This paper contrasts the human-microbial relations of two particular groups clustered around caring for the gut microbiome. From ethnographic work with practitioners of food fermentation in Toronto and online, I will discuss their concern for human-microbial relations and their wonder at the alchemical transformation from tea and sugar to kombucha or the pounding of cabbage to release juices to facilitate microbial ecologies for beneficial fermentation. I discuss those practices in tandem with the relations of microbial optimization discussed by direct to consumer microbiome test consumers. Here beneficial foods are entered on excel sheets of personalized advice and placed on fridge doors. Choosing correctly will allow the host’s body to become its best self. In each of these domains of care practices for the microbiome, I will present the possible relations between humans and microbes, that at times attempt to transgress extractive relations and at others emphasize the optimization and often financialization of microbes for human bodies and environments.

Toward Social and Epistemic Foundations of Molecular Systems Engineering: Evidence From European Scientific Consortia *Renan Gonçalves Leonel da Silva, Swiss Federal Institute of Technology in Zurich; Alessandro Blasimme, ETH Zurich*

Social Studies of Science has produced a robust literature characterizing contemporary discourses, practices, and promises of Synthetic Biology in twenty-first century. Simultaneously, the so-called Molecular Systems Engineering (MSE) grown significantly in European research institutions. MSE is a novel approach to clinical innovation that considerably expands the toolbox of regenerative medicine both technically and theoretically. Despite we can identify some sociotechnical processes described on the literature of Synthetic Biology as driving the research agenda setting in MSE, there is still a lack of dedicated analysis about what this field actually is. This article aims to present a comprehensive analysis of MSE in its institutional and epistemic dimensions, going further into the challenge to expand STS frameworks on Synthetic Biology. Addressing this objective, this is a merged qualitative-method research in which we applied scoping review and digital ethnographic tools to examine publications, reports, online materials and official digital content available in the web from three relevant European scientific consortia of MSE i.e. EPSRC Program Molecular Systems Engineering at Imperial College of London in UK, the SNSF NCCR Molecular Systems Engineering at University of Basel and ETH Zürich in Switzerland, and The Flagship Initiative Engineering Molecular Systems at University Heidelberg in Germany. By developing tools and devices to monitor and manipulate complex biochemical systems, this field is an interesting movement of integration between biological sciences and engineering research that deserves deeper investigation from STS and Philosophy of Science in Practice approaches

Session Organizer:

Sophia Rossmann, MCTS, Technical University of Munich

Chair:

Georgia Samaras, Munich Center for Technology in Society, Technical University of Munich

102. Practices And Methods Towards Good Relations With Robots And AI IV

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Participants:

Introducing practice theory into health care robotics. *Antonia Krummheuer, Aalborg University; Matthias Rehm, Aalborg University*

Due to the aging society, the number of people living with memory impairment will increase and put strains on health care systems all over the world. Reminder robots are seen as promising solutions. However, research in health care robotics is often based on psychological and cognitive traditions directed to mental processes and task completion. This neglects the humanistic perspective on how memory and reminding are related to individual's identities, local distributed practices, and the support of the assistive networks. The present talk will present findings from an ethnographic and participatory project in which we developed a reminder robot for and together with a person with severe memory loss, due to brain injury. We will review the design process combining practice theory (Nicolini, 2013; Reckwitz, 2010), STS (MacKenzie & Wajcman, 1999), and interaction analysis (Heath et al., 2010) to emphasize the relevance of social routines and locally distributed constructions of meaning that frame reminding practices and the meaning and use of robots. While classical reminder robots aim for triggering memory, we found that the main task of 'reminder robots' for people with severe memory loss is to support the individual's participation in a local and distributed reminding process with caretakers, (rather than reminding the individual to remember things s/he cannot remember). We argue for reframing the understanding what reminder robots are and can do and discuss how technology-driven values and political agendas can be addressed and reframed in humanistic and practice-based robotics.

Co-creation and values in designing and testing robotics for innovation and learning: insights from two case studies *Gianluigi Viscusi, Imperial College Business School*

This article aims to question the co-creation activities (Brandsen & Honingh, 2018; De Jaegher, Peräkylä, & Stevanovic, 2016; Lember, Brandsen, & Tönurist, 2019; Ramaswamy & Ozcan, 2018) and the values informing or rather forming their outputs, with a specific focus on technology innovation (Shilton, 2013; Snyder, Shilton, & Anderson, 2016; Stirling, 2008) in the domain of robotics. In particular, the different dimensions and perspectives on values are questioned from an STS perspective in their difference through the shapes that co-creation practices may assume once moving from, e.g., value intensive setting of local groups and communities to a population assuming the dimension of a crowd in co-creation practices characterized by seriality (Sartre, 1960; Viscusi & Tucci, 2018; Young, 1994). Also, the role of theoretical perspectives as user-centered design (Cavallo et al., 2018) and computational thinking (Wing, 2008) are questioned as elements making up of the mangle of practices (Pickering, 1993) that eventually translate values in infrastructures (Star, 1999) for robotics innovation and education. The theoretical arguments will be developed empirically through the analysis of two case studies: the Robotics Innovation Facility (RIF) based in Italy, where an ethnography has been carried out in 2018-2019, and a set of initiatives on educational robotics by the EPFL Center for Learning Science (LEARN), in Vaud, Switzerland observed in 2019-2020. Finally, the two cases are questioned as spaces where various actors eventually "enact" innovation (Barad, 2003), thus pointing out, the need for a social appraisal to inform the commitments to a robotics driven technological path (see also Stirling, 2008).

Deploying a Semi-society: Adaptations Inside Robotics Laboratories *Kuan-Hung Lo, Virginia Tech*

Laboratory life elaborates on the processes and activities that

take place in the laboratory space, such as constructing facts, grant writing, competition, and credibility building. Unlike Latour and Woolgar, I understand the robotics laboratory as a space in which environmental adaptations are demonstrated and social values for robots are constructed. My research highlights two strategies for transforming the laboratory into a semi-society: I-methodology and sampling. In using van Oost's I-methodology, I show that robotics engineers take their personal life experiences as significant cultural and environmental references for transforming their laboratories and building robots. Since these life experiences originate from their particular interactions with cultural/societal/environmental factors in society, particular social values and biases will therefore be embedded within the laboratory and the robot. The second strategy used by engineers in the laboratory is sampling. Sampling allows engineers to bring everyday environments, social values, and formations of items from society into the laboratory for testing. While conducting sampling intentionally or unintentionally, however, the engineers modify and reproduce particular cultural and environmental characteristics to change the laboratories. Meanwhile, sampling inserts these particular social values and environmental characteristics into the robots being designed and constructed. Because of I-methodology and sampling, the engineers build the laboratory with particular social values and environmental characteristics inhabiting the robots and their testing. I name this space as a "semi-society", which builds a partial reality while allowing the engineers to control variables. The robots the engineers design in this semi-society space are entangled with social values and environmental characteristics.

Session Organizers:

Andreas Bischof, University of Technology Chemnitz

Arne Maibaum, TU Berlin

103. Metaexpertise? STS, Metascience, and Data Science - III:

The Foundations of the Metascience Movement

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

The past decade has seen efforts to develop new forms of "domain-general" expertise such as metascience and data science. These have different motivations and intervene in specific fields in different ways—as interlocutors, partners, and, even, diagnosticians. Often, different forms of expertise establish distinct epistemic cultures in order to protect their autonomy and avoid the open conflicts that reveal rival epistemological commitments. However, interactions between domain-general and domain-specific forms of expertise have produced new conflicts. This raises challenging questions. Does the incursion of domain-general expertise represent a threat to the autonomy of disciplinary scientists? What would 'good relations' across this divide look like? How are domain-specific skills like embodied knowledge and practical judgment absorbed into domain-general systems meant to enumerate, evaluate, or automate scientific practice? The three sessions in this panel explore how these new "sciences of science" are transforming knowledge making.

Participants:

Kafka's Lab? Novel socio-bureaucratic arrangements in scientific and openness reforms *Bart Penders, Maastricht University*

To varying degrees, scientific fields are facing critiques of their credibility and have answered by introspective moments, yielding at least two types of epistemic outcomes: First, scientists have revisited and repeated seminal work in their field, or critically examine key characteristics of those and other studies in their field. Secondly, a select group of scientists have articulated new standards for methodology, communication and altruism aiming to prevent sub-par work from even taking place. These so-called science-on-science initiatives fuel both open science developments and scientific reform developments and often take an activist form. The proposed new horizons for science – reformed and open – are accompanied by novel

bureaucratic tools such as preregistration and registered reports, traceable data curation and sharing infrastructure and highly standardised modi operandi in the forms of methodological and reporting guidelines. Activists pushing this bureaucratic accountability infrastructure stress the improvements to the quality and validity of science as legitimations of the additional labour. Those critical of these developments, or in plain opposition, question the epistemic value they bring and argue that most of it pushes so called ‘check-list science’. This paper chronicles this ongoing dispute for the ‘soul of science’ and the emergent role of STS scholars in this debate with a focus on the new features in the ongoing bureaucratisation of science.

Self-Correction in Science: The Diagnostic and Integrative Motives for Replication *David Peterson, UCLA; Aaron Panofsky, University of California, Los Angeles*

Research replication, with its potential to diagnose the truth of scientific claims, is argued to be central to social control in science. Yet a series of frauds and failed replications have raised questions regarding the frequency and effectiveness of current practices. Metascientific activists have advocated policies that incentivize replications and make them more diagnostically potent. We argue that both current debates and previous research in the social studies of science have overlooked a key dimension of replication practice. Rather than diagnostic tests, replication is commonly motivated by a practical desire to extend research interests. This motivation for replication, which we label “integrative,” is characterized by a pragmatic flexibility toward protocols. The goal is to appropriate what is useful, not test for truth. Within many experimental cultures, however, integrative replications can produce replications of ambiguous diagnostic power. Based on interviews with 60 members of the Board of Reviewing Editors for Science, we show how the interplay between the diagnostic and integrative motives for replication differs between fields and produces different cultures of replication. We offer six theses that aim to put science studies and science activism into dialogue to show why effective reforms will need to confront issues of disciplinary difference.

Metascience, mess and misalignments *Martin Bush, University of Melbourne; Fiona Fidler, University of Melbourne; Nicole C Nelson, University of Wisconsin Madison; Uljana Feest, Leibniz Universität Hannover*

Over recent years, events like the “replication crisis” in psychology have led to a community of scholarly practitioners identifying as ‘metascientists’ or ‘metaresearchers’. In 2019, a symposium announced “the emergence of a new discipline called metascience”, defined as the “science of science”, prompting considerable skepticism within STS. Was that not exactly what we had been doing all these years? This raises questions of disciplinarity and situated knowledges. Usually, different forms of expertise simply talk past each other. What does it mean when they come into conflict? To what extent do we take seriously the motivations behind scholarly practices? STS itself is no stranger to such issues, having been described in the past variously as an interdisciplinary endeavour, a discipline in its own right and an unwanted incursion into the expertise of scientists. This roundtable discusses the rise of metascience and its relationship with other disciplines that ‘study science’, posing the following questions. In what ways are they similar or distinct? What are the historical, philosophical and sociological underpinnings of metascience? How are these contested within metascience and in broader scholarship of scientific practice? A broad range of perspectives will be included. Discussants include Fiona Fidler, a metascientist who has studied the history of statistical reform efforts in science, Nicole Nelson, an expert in the social studies of medicine and collaborating editor on Social Studies of Science, and Uljana Feest, a philosopher of science who has written about the concept of replication.

Session Organizer:

Fiona Fidler, University of Melbourne

Chair:

Fiona Fidler, University of Melbourne

104. Computational Media Technologies: Computing and Critique Beyond Disciplinary Configurations - IV

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Despite the ongoing interest in the history, epistemology, sociology, and cultures of computing and its defining practices (see Benjamin 2019, Mackenzie 2001, Roberge & Castelle 2020), the study of computational media remains largely dispersed across a wide range of discipline specific venues. Inspired by the more systemic examinations of computing advanced by fields like critical AI studies, indigenous STS, and media anthropology, however, this open panel brings together scholars who share a similar interest in understanding the transdisciplinary complexities, alternative histories, and political a priori behind computational media. With that intention in mind, we propose to consider computation as a paradigmatic ‘media technology’ whose entanglement with questions of both mediation and technoscience promises to renew the study of technical cultures at large. Computational media, we contend, provides a rich, boundary (defying) object around which the disciplinary perspective of media studies, history of technology, and science studies can be made to converge. Not only does computational media relate contemporary technoscience to the cybernetic and cyborgial origins of computing (see Haraway 1985, Hayles 1999, Medina 2011), it also forces us to consider mediation as a structuring principle of technoscientific cultures, practices, and epistemologies (see Kittler 1986, Chun 2011). To explore these questions, this open panel will stage a number of interdisciplinary conversations which will not only revisit dominant discourses surrounding the study of computational media, but also challenge the disciplinary frameworks in which they have been historically concentrated.

Participants:

The Computer is not a Visual Medium: Visual Methods for Computational Materiality *Jacob Gaboury, UC Berkeley*

In his widely influential 2004 work “Continuous Paper,” Nick Montfort offers a critique of our tendency to privilege the visual experience of computational media in our analysis and understanding of the digital, naming this bias “screen essentialism.” In many ways this critique formed the foundation for a sea change in the field of media studies, a shift away from representational analysis and toward the materiality of computational technology in hardware, software, and code. Yet this wholesale refusal of the screen has produced its own restrictions, particularly as computational technologies come to re-engage visual experience in new ways, from the “discorrelated” images of post-cinema and computational photography to the adversarial networks that enable machine vision and artificial intelligence. How might we re-engage visual methods for the analysis of digital media without presuming the centrality of our phenomenal perception to the function of computational systems? Taking up this task, this essay models visual methods for computational materiality through an analysis of the central role that computer graphics played in the development of the modern computer. Drawing on archival and materialist methods from my forthcoming book, I argue that while the computer is not a visual medium, computation itself has been shaped by a theory of relation that begins with the visual, and can be traced directly to contemporary applications in big data, cloud computing, and artificial intelligence. In pushing back against the critique of screen essentialism, my goal is to open up new avenues for visual methods in the study of computational media technologies.

Between Display and Memory: A Media Archaeology of Vacuum Tubes, 1897-1948 *Yijun Sun, University of Massachusetts Amherst*

This essay explores the evolutionary histories of vacuum tubes, especially the Braun tube, Cathode-Ray tube and Williams tube,

in their transformation from the television display system to the computer random-access memory and display system between 1897 to 1948. It contributes to research on media technology and the general “material turn”. In conversation with Kittler’s description of the three functions of media—processing, storage and transmission, this essay investigates how the needs of image processing and transmission in interaction with human vision inevitably led to the time manipulation of information storage. Making use of the secondary emission phenomenon, the vacuum tubes were used to store two distinct electrostatic charge states on computer screens that made the calculation of discrete information possible. Through a media archaeological investigation on vacuum tubes in this turning point, I argue that the way of mapping graphical information in a two dimensional mathematically space in computers had already existed in the oscilloscope and the radar screen in the evolution of television display tubes. Discrete logic is just a consequence of the discrete operational possibilities of electrical signals, that was long embedded in the process of improving wireless telecommunication in conquering time and space. This essay suggests comprehensive media histories that engage with electrical engineering and the operations of technical hardwares underlying human perceptions. Vacuum tubes’ ability to store, transmit and control electricity offers us a less human-centric perspective to look at the three functions of media in historical precision and interrelation.

Making the Laser Printer: Hewlett-Packard and Neoliberal Regimes of Use *Elisabeth Asher, University Of Maryland College Park*

In 1987, Hewlett-Packard released the LaserJet II, the second coming of the very first desktop printer, and, with it, a user manual emblazoned with a new version of Michelangelo’s Creation of Adam—God’s hand as HP, and Adam the printer, reaching eternally toward each other. In this paper, I use the manual, along with HP advertisements and grey material, to uncover the image or idea of printing that Hewlett-Packard sought to convey in their production of the printer. What had they created? And for what kind of user? Through close reading, ANT-informed analysis, and some archaeological excavation, I identify how these materials work together to create regimes of use for the printer, and how they act in different moments as oracle, as teacher, as prosthesis. Together, these texts make up a corporate heteroglossia—producing the user as clumsy and fallible, and the printer as well-greased, perfect, neutral—masking Hewlett-Packard’s market interests. This is a historically situated, archival, materialist history, but one that has repeated and will repeat again, as part of the breathless enthusiasm for and presumed apoliticism of computing and other technologies. I place the LaserJet within this broader context of global capital-ism and neoliberalism, and left populist or universalist politics within the U.S., to analyze how it and its maker, HP, are implicated in tech idealism, class relations, and corporate interests.

Latent Deep Space. Generative Neural Networks in the Sciences *Fabian Offert, University of California, Santa Barbara*

Recent spectacular successes of machine learning in the special sciences point to the emergence of a new techno-methodological “artificial intelligence” trading zone. The epistemological implications of this trading zone, however, have so far not been studied in depth. In fact, critical research on artificial intelligence systems has focused almost exclusively on the social use of machine learning. And while the political significance of applications like facial recognition and predictive policing has indeed warranted attention, the dominant focus on the explicitly political has produced a backlog of deeply flawed technical reality. Among the techniques that make up this backlog, one warrants particular attention from the perspective of media studies and visual studies: the generative adversarial network (GAN), a generative neural network that operates primarily on

image data. While GANs have been studied in the context of so-called “deep fakes” (so, again, as an explicitly political technique) their distinctive role in the sciences – in astronomy, medicine, chemistry, and biology – has gone largely unnoticed. In this paper, I argue that GANs introduce a set of concrete computational techniques into the scientific process that dissolve the traditional distinction between “computer simulation”, “computational photography”, and “computer graphics”: GANs are all of those things and none of those things at the same time. Thus, in GANs, scientific problems turn into image problems, and technical legacy determines epistemic faculty. I discuss this hypothesis in relation to established theories of images in the sciences, and recent applications of GANs to problems in astronomy and medicine.

Listening in the Afterlife of Data *David Cecchetto, York University, Canada*

Today, the privileged form of communication may well be that of computational data, which continues to circulate its fever dreams of universal exchange—its hallucinations of information that would remain the same as it moves between contexts—in the absence of anyone necessarily believing in its communicative alibi. And yet the alibi of communicative causality persists, suggesting that we are living in the afterlife of data. Data is just the latest form of the longstanding trope of the “impossibility of communication,” which has previously been demonstrated across disciplines ranging from Psychology to Information Theory. However, if this is a trope that variously appears in diverse historical and cultural settings it is also one who’s specific textures have not always been listened to as attentively as they might: (impossible) communications have their moments, contexts, trajectories, and promiscuities just as much as their (never actually existing) positive counterparts are purported to, and the densities, roughnesses, speeds, and buoyancies of these are as audible as anything else. One might listen, then, to the siren songs of smooth computational space in order to hear what is disclosed in and procured by the specifics of the alibi. In this talk, I introduce the concept of incommunication and develop it by listening to specific instances of computation, attending especially to the weird relationalities that obtain in their aesthetic dimensions. If my goals in doing so are in many senses theoretical, my methods are emphatically pragmatic: I will share the ways that specific listening engagements temporalize information in ways that cannot easily be described in predominant network models but that can be heard, a fact that in turn will open new questions about the morphologies, biologies, and temporalities of knowledge in relation to information.

Session Organizers:

Théo Lepage-Richer, Brown University
Ranjodh Singh Dhaliwal, University of Notre Dame

Chair:

Jacob Gaboury, UC Berkeley

105. Utilizing STS Pedagogies in Design Education – I

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

On June 9th, 2019, so-called “design ethicist” and former Google employee Tristan Harris, tweeted: “We need a new field of ‘Society & Technology Interaction’ (or STX).” The tweet caused a maelstrom of reactions from STS scholars and others, who used it as a classic example of the willful ignorance of industrial actors towards decades-old scholarship about their field. Harris eventually deleted the tweet and apologized for “a poor choice of words”: “We want to see a world where the field of design...[is] equipped with an applied view of the fields you mention.” This panel explores how this work is already being done and how it might continue. Arguably, Design Studies has been an STS field for over 35 years: in 1984, Hillier, Musgrove, and O’Sullivan argue that architecture should be taught alongside scientific philosophers such as Popper, Kuhn, and Lakatos; five years later, design theorist Victor Margolin uses Dickson, Feyerabend, and Aronowitz to argue that “we cannot conceive of any theory of

design...independent of a theory of society" (1989); and in 2015, Cameron Tonkinwise argues that Actor-Network Theory is inherently designerly. Design educators teach students to design artifacts which are necessarily embedded within sociotechnical and technoscientific systems. What, then, can STS offer the design academy? How can students connect their studio work with its broader implications? We aim to assemble a panel of teacher-scholars who will directly address pedagogical approaches.

Participants:

Borrow, Adapt, Embrace, Remake: How and What Design Pedagogy and Practice Should Steal From STS *Liese Zahabi, University of New Hampshire*

The 2017 version of The Handbook of STS offers the following, "Ultimately, science and technology shape how humans experience, imagine, assemble, and order the worlds they live in." (p1) The same can be said for the discipline(s) of design. However, the epistemic ways both disciplines harness words like technology, design, and science, to concepts like imagine, assemble, and order are tricky, nuanced, and often, overlapping. Vertesi et al describe this as "associated sites of scholarly intersection that constitute rich trading zones" (Handbook of STS, 2017, p 169). This metaphor of trade is an exceptionally helpful one as we consider the marooned siloes of academia—being exposed to the different customs, techniques, and wisdoms of another field offers new perspectives, the friction of rubbing together supplies sparks. Arguably, indeed, the discipline(s) of design have been utilizing ideas and techniques adjacent to STS for decades: situatedness, systems thinking and theory, the focus on contexts, and the study of process, methods, and tools of design. However, design pedagogy needs to expand the use of these techniques in order to help (paradoxically) both root and release design and its study in our contemporary moment. What we make through design greatly impacts culture and the planet, and urgently requires those doing the making to understand the implications of their choices, and the ways those choices are contextually nested. The field of STS offers an extant and expanding framework of methods to design faculty that can help shape the next generation of design thinkers and makers.

"Bridging" design and STS: Using Winner's "Do Artifacts Have Politics?" in design theory education *ginger coons, Willem de Kooning Academy*

Langdon Winner's "Do Artifacts Have Politics?" (1980) is a seminal text in STS, offering examples of the politics and ideologies that he argues are embedded in the titular artefacts. Perhaps the most prominent and repeated example in the text is that of the overpasses on the parkways of Long Island which, in Winner's telling, were planned with low overhead clearance in order to prevent busses from accessing certain parks and beaches. Winner's text has, over the years, sparked a cottage industry of debate, including "Do Politics Have Artefacts?" (1999) from Bernward Joerges, and "Do Artefacts Have Ambivalence?" by Woolgar and Cooper (1999). Aside from a lively debate in STS, Winner's text has a side-job in art and design, being frequently cited in prominent design journals and in sub-fields of design research concerned with morality, ethics, or user behaviour. It is also used as a text in various design schools. In this paper, we address the impact of Winner's bridges in undergraduate design theory classes at a major Dutch art and design academy. In these classes, the text is used as a jumping-off point for discussions and projects which ask students to envision the role of politics and ideologies in their work as designers and, to varying degrees, question the ideological commitments of their disciplines through hands-on theory assignments. This paper draws on student surveys, teacher interviews, and student projects to understand Winner's impact on student understandings of design disciplines as morally-charged or political.

Critical STS Pedagogy in Design Education: The Design, Innovation, and Society Major at Rensselaer *James Malazita, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute; Raquel Velho, Rensselaer*

Polytechnic Institute

We have often seen examples of undergraduate STEM and design education that propose a model of the "enlightened scientist/engineer/designer" through a consilience approach: building supplemental modules, dual majors or specializations within a major that teach students ethical issues, or social scientific and humanistic inquiry. At our Design, Innovation, and Society (DIS) program in the Department of Science & Technology Studies at RPI, we've taken a different approach to thinking about STS as critical pedagogy. Rather than thinking of STS 'with' design, STS is diffracted with design education to create its own model: STS as design. In this paper we will introduce DIS—the only undergraduate studio-based design program in the United States of America housed in a social science department. We discuss how our critical approach to STS as Design has offered a unique pedagogical experience, where students are trained not only to conceptualize how the world could and ought to be, but acquire the skills to make it so. Every semester, DIS majors take hands-on design studio classes which range from Industrial Design, Organizational Design, and Regenerative Design. All of these studios are taught by STS faculty members, who teach both design skills and critical reflections on the design process, capitalism, and cultures of innovation. Though they graduate with a degree from the STS Department, DIS students largely enter careers in product design, industrial design, engineering, and entrepreneurship. Having recently celebrated its twentieth anniversary, we present the DIS program as a radical-yet-sustainable model of critical STS pedagogical and curricular design.

Session Organizers:

Gabriel Schaffzin, York University, Toronto
Zachary Kaiser, Michigan State University

106. #TechOtherwise: Now is the time to Defund Big Tech and Refund Community

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Now is the time to radically redirect the future of tech. To think tech otherwise is to move away from binaries of tech or not in favour of how we could make tech differently, in the service of our collective and sustainable well being. Our goal with Tech Otherwise (<https://techotherwise.pubpub.org/>) is to create a space for activists, practitioners, citizens and scholars to share their work around critical technology themes. The recent report Defund Big Tech, Refund Community: Anti-Trust is Not Enough, Another Tech is Possible synthesizes the challenges posed by the way that the private technology sector is currently organized, and proposes how we can all collectively address them. The writing of the report also highlighted our desire to expand the body of work around critical technology and to share the communal energy with a broader audience. This roundtable expands the conversation beyond the authors of that report and discusses collective action paths for meaningful change to the trajectory of tech development, shifting a focus for action away from big tech industry alone to civic responsibility, infrastructuring, local and global community, collective action, and socially governed technology. In this roundtable, the four organizers from Tech Otherwise will facilitate a lively discussion with participants from the Tech Worker Coalition, Alphabet Workers, the Coalition for Critical Technology and others on how STS research and practice can meaningfully partner with other actors to shift the trajectory of technology into a more sustainable and just direction.

Presenters:

Lilly Irani, University of California, San Diego
Dawn Walker, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto
Alex Hanna, Google
Chelsea M Barabas, Massachusetts Institute for Technology (MIT)

Session Organizers:

Andrew Clement, University of Toronto

Christoph Becker, University of Toronto
EunJeong Cheon, Aalborg University
Pedro Reynolds-Cuellar, MIT

107. Diplomacy in a time of division, I

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Ours is a time of division and fractures—a time of crises. Given the urgent problems we must face, there is no guarantee on predicting how will the agents involved, both human and other-than-human, will respond, let alone forcing one set of conditions upon them, or using them at will. In fact, we can only be certain of the divergence of obligations and requirements of the diverse parts involved (Stengers 2011). The unstable and heterogeneous landscape of current and urgent problems calls for a radically different role for scientific practices. Their aim is not to neutralize divergences, securing one expert consensual take, but rather these practices must take part in a heterogeneous and ecological assembly. If scientific practices, along with their experts, are not to be the great deciders, what role should they play? How should they behave? In what terms must they present themselves? This is the central problem of diplomacy, as Isabelle Stengers (2011, 2020) understands it. Diplomacy is a device to render different voices equal—not interchangeable, but equally present—in every decision. A diplomatic practice comes out from a group and does not necessarily seek a common ground. Yet, they are all but undefined. Our aim is to consider the political impact that different practices—related to ecological and social problems, multispecies conversations, methodological aspects of STS, or others—could have and how would they behave when rooted in diplomacy.

Participants:

Diplomacy, science, and fiction *Juan Felipe Guevara-Aristizabal*, *Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana-Cuajimalpa, México*

Isabelle Stenger's diplomatic task has a long history whose beginning could be traced back to her experience as a chemist working with philosophical questions in a thermodynamics laboratory. However, the eruption of diplomacy in her philosophical discourse in the mid-90s appears at the crossroads of very heterogeneous interests: there is a historical thread manifestly interested in a different narrative for the history of physics after the Galileo event and the invention of modern science, there is a philosophical thread under the sign of an ecology of practices and the birth of cosmopolitics, and there is a sociological thread contingently marked by the famous science wars episode. Despite being rooted in those peculiar conditions of the 1990s, this is just the beginning for a long road ahead. Diplomacy, hence, is endeavored with the complex and problematic task of not leaving anything behind—a sheer act of speculation, following Alfred N. Whitehead's proposal. In this talk, I will try to approach some of the key insights related to this beginning of diplomacy, as well as other beginnings, other threads that appear in later developments. Particularly, there is an interest in the place of fiction within this diplomatic meshwork. Throughout the last two decades, Stengers has used scientifiction and science fiction as ways to approach a narrative aspect of diplomacy, one that seems very relevant in the face of the many socio-environmental crises happening nowadays. How a story is told and how the characters are framed and presented is a delicate diplomatic matter.

multiple worlds of depression: a case of intercultural mental health in Chile *Jorge Atanasio Gallardo*, *Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

Depression is an issue of global concern. In response, Global Mental Health and Transcultural Psychiatry has emerged as analytical and comprehensive options. However, even though sociology could contribute to this discussion, not enough debates have been elaborated on how to address this phenomenon beyond social constructionism and cultural relativism. Therefore, to go beyond these positions, I incorporate tools from Social Studies of Science (STS) to investigate how depression is enacted in an

intercultural mental health service in Chile. From the theoretical sensitivity of political ontology, I explore the problems produced by the great modern-western assumption: the existence of one nature and many cultures. Among my results, I have seen that what is called "depression" and "interculturality" are far from being univocal and stable entities. On the contrary, they are in constant dispute, where both humans and non-humans interact to bring their existences into reality. Therefore, I discuss the supposed relationships between mind-body, mind-brain, body-nature and nature-culture, which frame the existence of what we currently call depression and the global responses to its approach, and the importance of STS sensitivity to study issues such as depression, beyond a modern Western understanding.

Narrating Autoimmunity: Functional medicine and patient biography *Kalindi Vora*, *University of California Davis*

How can attention to patient narratives by functional medicine (FM) practitioners address the impact of experience of racism and sexism on patients with autoimmunity? Centering ethnography and STS attention to culture's potential to shift medical concepts over time (Haraway 1988, 1991; E. Martin 1990; Weasel 1994) this paper examines the potential of patient-centered FM collaborative relationships and coproduced knowledge to shift mainstream medicine's approach to chronic illness. This study is part of a multi-year research project that uses methods from STS to explore how experiences of structural discrimination due to race and gender may function to predispose patients to autoimmune disease. 5-10% of the global population will have autoimmune disease in their lifetime, and severity of symptoms correlates with experiences of racism and sexism (Chae 2019). Integrative approaches in FM create space to attend to the individual sensitivities of a patient's body, and to include attention to medical narrative and personal biography in ways that might accommodate data on racism and sexism. Patients, empowered (though sometimes also misled) by integrative treatments, go back to their general practitioners with new knowledge and questions after learning about alternate lab ranges and fuller panels of testing that are possible outside of the world of HMOs. Bringing together analysis of historical changes in medicine's conceptual apparatus with the feminist science push for personalizing practice to control cultural for researcher bias raises the potential for medicine to better diagnose and treat the chronic impact of structural injustice on the health of historically excluded groups.

(In)capacity to respond: an ethnographic exploration of COVID-19's front line in southern Ecuador *Maka Suarez, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography; Fu Yu Chang, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*

In March 2020, Ecuador became the epitome of a failed response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Intensive Care Units collapsed; bodies piled up in make-shift morgues, in local cemeteries, and even on the streets of Guayaquil, Ecuador's largest city port. Nearly a year later, exhausted medical workers had managed to control the worst part of the pandemic despite limited capacity, ill-equipped hospitals, and a chronically underfunded health system. In this piece we ethnographically approach the life of COVID-19's front line workers in southern Ecuador based on ten months of research in one of its rural counties. We are interested in exploring three approaches to response capacity to COVID-19: medical workers ability to deal with the pandemic (infrastructural capacity within Ecuador), the country's economic possibilities to respond (scale of the pandemic), and the politics behind the pandemic's management (health governance). Together, these themes illuminate the struggles to respond to a pandemic as well as the spaces of improvisation that are necessary to face a public health crisis in low resource countries, even more so in rural areas. In following the study of other "crises" and disasters, we argue for the need to look beyond the totalizing narratives of "the pandemic" by exploring the intricate ways in which health, economy and politics become enmeshed and pan out in the lives

of everyday citizens.

Session Organizers:

Juan Felipe Guevara-Aristizabal, Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana-Cuajimalpa, México

Agustín Mercado, Centro de Investigaciones Interdisciplinarias en Ciencias y Humanidades, UNAM

Chair:

Agustín Mercado, Centro de Investigaciones Interdisciplinarias en Ciencias y Humanidades, UNAM

108. Technologies for claiming our kin - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

The infrastructure and practices for administering colonization, slavery, and capitalist heritable property relations are the basis for proliferating genealogical technologies, from DNA databases to family tree websites. These technologies materially and socially support white settler genealogical practices that identify away from responsibilities for the material conditions and effects of whiteness, and towards race shifting and the appropriation of racialized identities. However, increasingly people are also developing projects for claiming kin that do not erase the histories and ongoing practices of land theft, genocide, enslavement, and border militarism. The two sessions for “Technologies for claiming our kin” investigate data, stories, material practices, and dreaming that allow people to claim kin other than the typical history of genealogy. What are the forms of relationality through which people might “claim bad kin,” or collect their relations when their relations are the agents of tremendous harm? What practices of claiming kin resist the social organization of forgetting of histories, familial and otherwise, that fall outside the settler state’s conception of being related? How do we build relationality in new kin formations, and what social and technical practices support such work? These sessions address human and non-human, microbial and chemical, technical and social infrastructures of relationality.

Participants:

Bad Relations: Sociology Of ‘Authoritative’ Communities And Writing Histories Of Physical Anthropology In Mexico
Francisco Vergara-Silva, Instituto de Biología, Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

Select episodes and scattered incidents related to the history of physical anthropology in Mexico—all useful to understand discourses on ‘race’ and racist practices in that country during the 20th century—have been addressed by an increasing number of scholars in recent years. In the aftermath of the ‘Mexican mestizo genome project’, when neocolonial, extractivist human population genomic studies involving Mexican samples have been finally integrated to mainstream transnational research coordinated from Global North metropolises, is it possible to envision writing projects related to the history of ‘race’/racism in (and out of) Mexican physical anthropology that connect interdisciplinary trajectories of ‘individuals, ideas and institutions’, and at the same time preserve a meaningful sense of local/national situatedness? In this paper, I address this issue through a review of my own published research on the conflicts and controversies—or ‘bad relations’—in which Juan Comas Camps (1900-1979), the ‘dean of modern Mexican physical anthropology’, was involved both nationally and as part of international networks. Reviewing that case study facilitates an appraisal (largely ethnographic, sociological) of the currently active community of professional physical anthropologists and their colleagues in the humanities—mostly historians and philosophers of science—self-appointed as ‘authorities’ on the matter. I argue that some of their ideological stances—which reflect conservative tendencies present in the ‘Comas case’—are a primary obstacle for the pursuit of relevant historiographic and/or STS projects. I also suggest that the latter might be best attainable from external vantage points (e.g. from exile) or associated circumstances.

Biological Birth Right: Blood, Genes, and the Transmission of Citizenship in the Immigration and Nationality Act
Chloe Sariago, Yale University

How do new reproductive technologies impact who counts as a citizen in children born from the transnational fertility trade? This paper examines the Immigration and Nationality Act (INA) and its “hetero-normalization of sex-cells” in birthright citizenship cases adjudicated in the United States using socio-legal discourse analysis from a data set of 78 U.S. citizenship cases. Birthright citizenship is the most privileged form of citizenship in the U.S. Acquiring citizenship status through birth grants privileges not accessible through the process of naturalization. With the court decision legalizing same-sex marriage in 2015—a legal and symbolic motion to incorporate LGBTQ+ families into the benefits of marriage—non-heteronormative family, kinship, and reproductive forms have proliferated in the mainstream. Part of this rise in non-heteronormative family-building has accompanied a rise in the use of assisted reproductive technologies (ART) by same-sex parents. However, the recent denial of citizenship to one twin brother due to a failure to prove a DNA relationship to one of his two fathers in *Dvash-Banks v. Pompeo* (2018) has sparked a necessity for re-examining the INA’s role in organizing birthright citizenship, genetics, family formations, and developments in reproductive technologies. Given that developments in fertility treatments can now include the genetic material of up to three people (using mitochondrial manipulation), the bodies of up to 4 (if using IVF with a surrogate), and the administrative and medical input from at least a dozen more, the latent ideal of a “nuclear family” in U.S. immigration policy must be re-examined.

Disciplining kinship: Medical Illustration and the Institutionalization of Whiteness
Drew Danielle Belsky, STS Program, York University

Disciplinary histories recapitulate settler genealogies: father figures beget schools with a family resemblance, academic lineages produce intellectual pedigrees and construct claims to credible knowledge as heritable traits. Banu Subramaniam has explored the persistent undercurrents of eugenics in evolutionary biology and how “these complex histories are entirely erased within disciplinary histories” (2014, p. 67). Similarly, the training of professional medical illustrators in North America overlooks its foundations in both unequal gender relations and colonial classification of bodily difference. In this paper, I examine how conceptual models based in white settler kinship structures shape disciplinary narratives and the material practices of contemporary (bio)medical illustrators. Drawing on ethnographic and archival research, my research builds on feminist STS and critical disability studies to make sense of how expertise and agency are negotiated in this female-dominated paramedical field. Whether grounded in patriarchal lineage or epistemic affinities, kinship metaphors are deployed in ways that elide frictions and structural inequalities in favour of unifying narratives of belonging. An origin story grounded in father figures obscures the administrative and bureaucratic production of a profession by female medical illustrators in the twentieth century. However, recuperation of female figures in science runs the risk of reinforcing categories of race and gender and of glossing over the ways in which white women have contributed to colonial projects of dominance through the institutionalization of whiteness. By claiming these knotty figures, my project seeks to disrupt the colonial categories and moralities built into the production of disciplinary kin and of medical bodies.

Session Organizer:

Alexis Shotwell, Carleton University

Discussant:

Scout Calvert

109. Rethinking Outer Space And Science: Critical Engagements With The Cosmos And The Extra-terrestrial - IV

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

Digging Outer Space: Amateurs' Participation to Science Though Data and Images *Maxime Harvey, Université du Québec à Montréal (UQAM)*

In March 2012, the European Space Agency lunched a contest called Hubble's Hidden Treasure. To exploit the more than a million observations of the Hubble Space Telescope, the agency invited the public to dig its archive, play with its data and compete for prizes. How were relations between amateurs and other actors reimagined through this process (e.g., scientists, technicians, educators, journalists, the general public, but also non-human actors such as astronomical objects, the telescope instruments, its data and resulting images)? How was the exercise of power established/resisted/negotiated among them? Were practices such as searching the archive, processing its data and sharing pictures normalized with it? How was their work acknowledged in terms of scientific participation, digital engagement and visual creation? Finally, how did amateurs understand their contribution to the contest? This paper will present a critical review of this event by looking at both the institutional representation of amateur's participation to the contest and, through traces and interviews, the representation of the "actual" practices of amateurs who participated. It is influenced by Rose's critical visual methodology and Cartwright's materialist approach to visual science studies. This study is part of a larger research on the appropriation of Hubble's data by amateur astronomers. It aims to contribute to social studies of outer space and the understanding of scientific practices of representation. The novelty of this paper is to discuss how practices of representation of outer space may affect the public participation of amateurs in astronomy.

International Space Technology Projects and Inclusive Development: Can We Have Good Relations Between Participating Stakeholders? *Devyani Gajjar, The Open University*

Applications of space technologies in international development projects are emerging, such as the use of remote sensing data to predict malaria outbreaks or plan for disasters. When implemented, such projects could widen relational power inequalities for those excluded from the benefits of space applications through more powerful stakeholders retaining the ability to control technological resources. Furthermore, external space applications designed for local problems can centre epistemologies of the Global North while displacing marginalised communities' knowledges. Space projects often work within the framework of the Sustainable Development Goals, which have been questioned over their ability to engage with power relations between stakeholders. Therefore, it is necessary to critically evaluate if good relations between stakeholders in space projects can occur, such as inclusive development for project beneficiaries, redistributing power over resources and recognising multiple knowledges. This work in progress paper investigates whether space projects can be designed and implemented to foster good relations between participating stakeholders. The framework of inclusive innovation will be used to evaluate space projects in the International Partnership Programme (IPP), which is led by the UK Space Agency and funded by the UK government's Official Development Assistance budget. Data collection methods include document analysis and semi-structured interviews with project members and beneficiaries. Preliminary findings indicate that unsustainable funding resources pose significant barriers to fostering good relations. These findings could bring improved insights into if and how space projects can be governed to

support inclusive development and social justice for those excluded from the benefits of space applications.

Polar space infrastructures and their entanglements *Eleanor Armstrong, University of Delaware*

Addressing Outer Space infrastructures in the polar regions, my paper focuses on the entanglements of space research, imaginaries of the Arctic, and geopolitical power. Throughout, I use the analytic tool of 'sacrifice zones' to understand the ways interactions are framed in public discourse, engaging it conceptually to foreground the impacts of terrestrial space science research, rather than seeing these as secondary concerns. Exploring the actions of the Grise Fiord community on Devon Island in the early 2000s around Land use by Mars Society Habitat project and NASA's Haughton-Mars Project; I emphasise the possibilities of the conceptual tool, impacts on local communities and researchers, and the overarching ways imaginaries about geographical locations – such as 'the Arctic' can shape how these play out.

Recycled and Repurposed Infrastructure for Space Science: The case of radio astronomy in Africa *Siri Lamoureaux, University of Siegen, Germany; James Lawrence Merron, University of Basel*

Moving away from conceptions of observatories and satellite launch sites as 'empty spaces' (Walker & Chinigò 2018) with no history and no people, this paper discusses radio astronomy as having a history, enduring material infrastructures and a social life. Based in South Africa, the Square Kilometre Array (SKA) is the biggest science project on the African continent and the largest scientific instrument in the world. In 2017, 'good relations' were strengthened with Ghana when the South African Department of Science and Technology - through the Renaissance Fund - transformed a ground-based satellite on the outskirts of Accra into a radio telescope, the first of nine telescopes to participate in the AVN (Africa Very Long Baseline Interferometry Network). During two years of repairs to telescopes in South Africa, the late Michael Gaylard scoured Google Earth for redundant telecommunications infrastructures in Africa which could be transformed into space science infrastructure. What resulted was an active "reimagining of interpersonal and inter-institutional relations surrounding space science infrastructures and environments" on the African continent. The aim of this paper is to analyse the advancement of radio astronomy on the African continent in terms of recycling and repurposing, providing a partial answer to the question: "what does science, technology and innovation mean from Africa"? (Mavhunga 2017). Looking at the AVN in this way we present the material politics and practices that have developed to mediate between unequal stakeholders, such scientists and residents who occupy land near these extremely sensitive observatories.

Session Organizer:

Eleanor Armstrong, University of Delaware

Discussant:

Julie Michelle Klinger, University of Delaware

110. The algorithmic turn of prediction - IV

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Throughout history, the future has been an important reference for mankind. Its role for life in the present, however, has changed significantly in the course of time. While the future was initially found to be unalterable, with the development of modern societies it became to be understood as an open horizon that stands in a causal relationship to the present – the future got shapable according to actions and decisions in the present. This shift in terms of interpreting the future made it even more attractive than before to produce knowledge about it. Predictive strategies subsequently flourished and technologies thereby played an increasingly important role. With the advent of modern forms of algorithmic data analysis, with machine

learning and artificial intelligence gaining center stage, another shift in referring to the future is likely, presenting an exciting as well as urgent challenge for social sciences in general and STS in particular. Before this backdrop, this panel aims to discuss the theoretical as well as empirical implications of algorithmic prediction in the datafied society. What effects does the algorithmization of prediction have on the systems, settings and situations concerned? How do algorithmic predictive technologies differ from their – allegedly less sophisticated – technological predecessors? And, last but not least, where are the analytical possibilities and limits of STS approaches regarding the algorithmic turn of prediction?

Participants:

From Statistical Uncertainty to Individual Prediction. Does Algorithmic Prediction Challenge the Open Future? *Elena Esposito, Bielefeld University*

Algorithmic prediction using machine learning and big data is very different from the idea of prediction that established itself in modern society since the 18th century, oriented and guided by the calculus of probability. Whereas probability calculus offers a rational way to deal with uncertainty, algorithms claim to provide a score for individual persons or singular events. This breaks with the modern view of an open future, that is unknowable for everyone because it does not yet exist. The paper analyses the consequences of the new forms of focused prediction on the different social structures that still rely on our shared uncertainty about the future. Besides unprecedented forms of control, the use of opaque machines require a new awareness of problems of solidarity, risk and prevention.

The « Divinatory » Power of Algorithms : From Prediction to Preemption of Behaviours *Christophe Lázaro, UCLouvain*

The spectacular development of algorithmic systems capable of collecting, analyzing and processing massive quantities of data have arguably conferred on humans a new device of prediction allowing to optimize decision-making processes, to anticipate risks and to exercise control over individuals. Drawing inspiration from divinatory practices of classical Antiquity as described in Cicero's Treatise De Divinatione, this contribution sheds light on the contemporary beliefs in the predictive power of algorithms. Through a cross-examination of ancient divinatory practices and contemporary algorithmic systems, it aims to clarify the rationalities that are intrinsic to operations on signs or data. In that respect, I will show that the current criticisms addressed to predictive algorithms are strongly reminiscent of those that, during Graeco-Latin antiquity, were formulated against mantic and divinatory practices by the first representatives of an emerging science. It is as if today one needs once again to replay the epistemological and ontological match opposing rational and irrational, primitive and modern, analogic and causal thinking, by questioning the irrational part of scientific constructions as well as the pragmatic and immanent logics of non-scientific conceptions of the world.

Session Organizers:

Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld

Elena Esposito, Bielefeld University

Chair:

Maximilian Heimstädt, Bielefeld University

111. Better Relations With/In Site and Space: Queer and Indigenous Interventions As Scientific Practice

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Critical feminist STS has constructively challenged the cisheteronormativity and white supremacy embedded in an array of sciences, from animal behavior to toxicology to urban ecology (Visperas, Brown, and Sexton 2016; Cipolla, Gupta, and Rubin 2017; Hoover 2017). This panel builds from these critiques to highlight emerging shifts—despite ongoing obstacles—within contemporary scientific methods and practices, focusing on field sites and laboratory spaces. We recognize that even those

practitioners committed to queering and decolonizing scientific knowledge production face entrenched systems of hierarchy and linearity. And yet, we also sense fantastic(al) potential. For instance, what pathways to environmental justice do queer ecological and Indigenous studies perspectives enable us to see, feel, and traverse? Or, focusing on the embodied experience of doing work in the field/lab in a specific body, what dangers and risks does this work entail? What would making space for BIPOC, queer, and trans scientists to do this work make possible, in terms of scientific outcomes, community engagement, and environmental justice action? We are especially interested in how queer and trans perspectives on cisheteronormativity might intersect with Indigenous studies and political ecological analyses of private property and public lands. For example, how can field science work within tribal protocols to disrupt settler science's longstanding practice of contributing to dispossession (through creation of conservation areas and parks, advancement of forestry and agriculture, river damming, etc.)? What critical modes of attention do queer and trans theories bring to the study of toxins and/or ecological "purity," across both urban and rural landscapes?

Participants:

A Case Study of Bodily Normativity in California's Wildfire Governance *Yanin Kramsky, University of California at Berkeley*

This research is located at the cutting edge of two contemporary problems: climate change-induced disasters and disaster governance that produces uneven outcomes across bodies. 'Bodily normativity' is used as an analytical lens because it encompasses complex situations that are crucial to navigate, yet remain unaccounted for, during disasters. Activists who foreground non-normative bodies (e.g., disabled, gender diverse, and elderly) consider wildfire governance a key disaster issue to mobilize around. The extent to which they are able to shape this political terrain is examined as unprecedented wildfires, smoke plumes, and precautionary power shutoffs that halt electricity to life-sustaining devices infiltrate communities. The San Francisco Bay Area is an exemplary multi-site where dry forests, growth-based development, and longstanding activism—from critical disability to transgender justice—converge. To understand how knowledge and meaning are constructed, codified, and circulated within this domain, a discursive analysis is used to investigate the following questions: How does bodily normativity operate across wildfire institutions in the Bay Area? In what ways does the operation of bodily normativity shape physical sites and impact as well as produce individuals with non-normative bodies? And, how is the political terrain of wildfire governance co-constituted by practitioners and activists while producing distinct political subjectivities among them? By bringing the analytical lens of bodily normativity to scholarship on the political ecology of wildfire governance, as well as an empirical case of disaster governance to queer geographical and critical environmental justice literatures, this project enriches understandings of embodied marginalization in the face of climate change.

Ice on the Moon: Colonizing Otherworlds *Jen Rose Smith, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Since early polar exploration, ice has been described as otherworldly, celestial, and unearthly. These descriptions were paired with the interpreted barren and lifeless aspects of ice-geographies. Today, however, ice is understood as integral to the future of human life, and not just for a changing climate on planet Earth. This talk will focus on ice as frozen water and analyzes the ways that this substance is figured as a precondition for the colonization of outer space. Ice is being hunted across our solar system and found on the moon and Mars, and its existence is hailed as a precondition for human life to survive in alternative, future worlds. Yet, those alternative worlds are imagined and funded by the wealthiest people and organizations on the planet (e.g. Jeff Bezos, Elon Musk, and the Department of Defense), leaving one to wonder who might be invited to repopulate or colonize such otherworlds. These developing

contexts give a modern, icy spin to the racial politics of the 1969 Apollo 11 mission critique of “no hot water, no toilets, no lights / but Whitey’s on the moon” by Gill Scott Heron.

Scientific Data, Relationality, and Decolonization *Charles Hahn, University of Washington*

Scholars and designers writing about the politics of informational technoscience have argued for “making kin with the machines”: advancing decolonizing by building AI and scientific projects with “good relations” (Lewis, Arista, Pechawis and Kite 2018). Science studies has shown that not only is science by nature relational (Latour 1984), but also that it is aware of and constantly responding to such relations in the everyday doing of scientific work (Edwards 2010). If such is true, then neither relationality nor reflexivity are by themselves sufficient for a social justice oriented or decolonial technoscience. This raises questions about what constitutes “good” relations vis a vis a decolonial technoscience. In contrast to prescriptions for technoscience to be relational and reflexive at the level of epistemology, this paper argues that what makes “good” technoscientific relations (i.e. advancing decolonization) are those projects that are aimed at addressing the concrete political and material needs of Indigenous people and institutions. A start to such an approach is to be found in decolonizing methodologies (Smith) and critical data scholars that emphasize engagement with ‘data sovereignty’ and ‘Indigenous protocols’ for research (Hetoevéhotohke’e Lucchesi 2020). A consequence of these observations is the deemphasis of the domain of “knowledge production” and the epistemic as a privileged realm for the production of (de)colonial relations in favor of more traditional social domains. The paper bases these reflections on ethnographic material with a group of scientists and Indigenous advocates building a database around salmon in Alaska.

Session Organizers:

Melina Packer, University of California, Riverside
Ashton Wesner, Colby College
Cleo Woelfle-Erskine, UW Seattle

112. Relations and Troubles of Tools of Valuation – IV

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

Higher rents for higher standard? Municipal housing tenants’ strategies to challenge the understanding of standard, quality and value in renovation projects. *Elena Bogdanova, University of Gothenburg*

The research within valuation studies, in particular on product quality and value, had shown how judgments of quality are socially constructed through different market tools (see e.g. Beckert and Musselina 2013). Higher quality is often seen as a reason for higher value. In this paper I will focus at the case where there is no unanimous understanding of “better quality”. Rental housing market in Sweden is simultaneously highly regulated and liberalised. The quality of rental apartments is often discussed in relation to “reconstructing” or “repairing” the living standard of half a century old buildings and raising it to the present day level and requirements to be able to charge higher rent. The standard increase is not directly related to the costs of renovation, but to a specific set of evaluative principles, and consequently leads to dramatic rent increase. In this paper I will discuss how the concept of “quality” is contested by different interest groups during consultation group meetings in the process of renovation of municipal rental housing in Gothenburg. I will show how the discussions on quality can be enriched by opposing it to the concept of “higher standard”. Empirically I analyse renovation projects in two suburbs of Gothenburg, and focus on how tenants are “redefining” the concept of standard in relation to “quality” to prevent rent increase. Ethnographic observations, interviews with tenants and representatives of

managing companies, and policy documents are the source of the empirical data.

Business Models, Public Value and the Magic Triangle.

Navigating Valuation In Urban Planning *Claudia MENDES, MCTS, Technical University of Munich*

Historically, urban planning and public policy in Germany and beyond has been closely intertwined with the principle of *Daseinsvorsorge*: The idea that the state should provide and grant equal access to basic goods and services such as water, energy, housing, mobility, education or culture emerged in the 1930s as a direct response to increasing industrialization and urbanization (Forsthoff 1938), and became legally enshrined as a municipal responsibility. The tools and practices of urban planners (e.g. cost-benefit-analysis) to justify public expenditure or to determine the value of specific public goods and services, have since been shaped by this principle, and so has the self-understanding of practitioners. More recently however, cities - often under the label of ‘smart cities’ - are increasingly called upon to become participants in innovation processes and to adopt a more entrepreneurial approach to urban development using new tools of ordering and valuation, such as business models. Through an ethnographic case study of the encounter between urban planners involved in an EU-funded smart city consortium and researcher-consultants from one of Europe’s leading business schools around a business model innovation tool called Business Model Navigator, I explore: How are established urban planning practices and tools of valuation challenged by the introduction of the business model tool and vice versa? When the planners start using the Business Model Navigator’s center-piece – the magic triangle –, controversies about the ‘quantifiable’ and the ‘valuable’ arise and eventually result in a radical reconfiguration of the tools and relations between the involved actors.

Bureaucratising Urban Nature: Territorialisation of Nature Environments by Working Numbers *Ask Greve Johansen, Aalborg University Copenhagen; Jens Iuel-Stissing, Aalborg University Copenhagen*

In recent decades the search for new forms of experimental governance has emerged in literature on urban governance. These types of governance have been promoted as necessary tools for grasping and responding to the fundamental and integrated social- and environmental sustainability challenges facing urbanisation in the 21 st century. An underlying premise of these governance approaches is that traditional bureaucratic modes of planning are neither capable of seeing problems facing contemporary urban life nor of envisioning the solutions to these problems. In this paper, we suggest that bureaucracies are indispensable components of future sustainability transitions because they enable the urban fabric to be worked upon systematically. From this premise, we investigate the planning bureaucracy as a site where new ways of seeing and acting upon urban reality are assembled. More specifically, we investigate how planners in Copenhagen arrange the production of numbers to render urban nature into new actionable territory for urban planning. Exploring number work, we posit, is crucial to make sense of how planning bureaucracies engage with the challenges facing contemporary urban life.

The Value of “Patrimoine”: Governing the Ageing of Infrastructures with the National Road Observatory *Roman Solé-Pomies, Center for the Sociology of Innovation - Mines ParisTech*

This paper investigates forms of valuation in the governing of large infrastructures. In the 2010s, the French state withdrew its previously ubiquitous technical services, leaving road management with territorial governments and roadworks companies. Yet, public bodies and private companies questioned the awareness of local governments, regarding the substantial maintenance work that ageing infrastructures are worth. They created the National Road Observatory (ONR), dedicated to

“knowing” and “preserving” road networks. Drawing on interviews at the ONR and in local authorities, as well as an analysis of their working documents, I discuss the interplay between the quantification work of the Observatory and the valuation problem it is meant to tackle. The ONR strives to correlate the states of roads with maintenance and management practices. Every year, territorial governments are asked to fill in spreadsheets with accounting data about roadworks, and forms with indicators regarding the physical dimensions and states of roads. These statistics are expected to prove that roads are valuable and deserve to be well maintained. This notably entails the valuation of past management, which enacts the infrastructure’s fragility and its manager’s responsibility. In institutional discourses surrounding the Observatory, roads are referred to using the French word “patrimoine”, which conveys not only the sense of an asset bringing future benefits, but also that of a legacy. The form of valuation at play at the ONR interestingly matches this duality. As it acknowledges the value of past work, quantification appears as a particular mode of attachment, intended to secure a transferred responsibility.

Replacing the Irreplaceable: Conflicting Valuation of Damage of Historic Buildings hit by the Mexico 2017 Earthquakes
Daniel Fridman, The University of Texas at Austin;
Benjamin Ibarra - Sevilla, The University of Texas at Austin;
Eldad J. Levy, The University of Texas at Austin

This paper examines the valuation of cultural heritage assets as a social, technical, and institutional process in the context of natural disasters. As the recent literature on valuation shows, assigning value when dealing with ‘invaluable goods’ is a simultaneously moral and technical process. The choice and use of a valuation technique may depend on socially shared meanings, institutions, established forms of expertise, power struggles, legal frameworks, culturally acceptable uses of money, and on the standing of the valued good in society. We use the case of the September 2017 earthquakes in Mexico, which damaged over two thousand historic monuments, including many churches, chapels, and monasteries that are federal property but are used by local congregations. After the disaster, officials at the National Institute of Anthropology and History (INAH) had to assess the value of damage in order to pursue funding from federal disaster relief and private insurance. But valuing damage for restoration implies defining it and understanding the uses of the heritage asset, and therefore indirectly valuing heritage itself. We examine how officials at the INAH, the insurance company, and local communities ascribe values to the damage of cultural heritage, and thus negotiate their understanding of what restoration of the damage means and entails in a context of massive losses and low institutionalization of valuation procedures. Data comes from 19 in-depth interviews with a variety of Mexican professionals, including preservation experts, architects, conservators, contractors, and other public officials in the field of heritage management.

Session Organizers:

Kristin Asdal, TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture

Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna

Chair:

Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech

113. Plenary - Presidential Plenary

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: Auditorium

Presidential Plenary - Joan

Participant:

Presidential Plenary *Joan Fujimura, University Of Wisconsin-Madison*

Presidential Plenary

Session Organizer:

Joan Fujimura, University Of Wisconsin-Madison

114. Moving beyond Histories of Technoscience rooted in Nationalism towards Transnational Histories of Entanglement, Connection and Mutual Influencing

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Participants:

Automating Discovery and the Gateway to the World: NASA, Mars, and the Philippines through the Transpacific Histories of the Internet
Maya Cruz, University of California - Davis
NASA is advancing artificial intelligence and machine learning to create autonomous capabilities for their Mars exploration rovers through online citizen science initiatives like A14Mars. What is at stake for building more socially just futures given NASA’s drive for what is described as “autonomous scientific discovery” and the long history of US imperial interests in scientific exploration? To respond, my research reads A14Mars through US colonial histories in the Philippines and their relation to the transpacific histories of the Internet. A14Mars enables anyone with Internet access to train NASA’s rovers as a citizen scientist by labeling datasets of Martian terrain images for SPOC, NASA’s algorithm for autonomous terrain classification and navigation. I argue that globalized technologies like the Internet have enabled the displacement of scientific labor at new scales, accelerating the classification, and thus capture, of space for US political economic interest through new technologies of computer vision and systems of autonomous terrain classification, which are predicated on technoliberal imaginaries and world orders (Atanasoski and Vora, 2018). Centering Warwick Anderson’s (2009) attention to the need for a postcolonial reading of Bowker and Star’s (1999) work on information infrastructure and classification, I read the history of the Internet in the Philippines through the NASA Ames Research Center (the “gateway to the world” to the Philippines), examining how designs for autonomous classification systems are globalized systems of information technology organized by global racial capitalism (Irani and Dourish, 2009) that reproduce gendered, racialized, classed, and imperial logics about labor, and scientific knowledge, and progress.

Coronized lives: COVID-19 and the de-politicization of masses
David Ngendo-Tshimba, Uganda Martyrs University

The prolonged COVID-19 lockdown in Uganda is extracting a huge toll on the people’s resilience. Although the pandemic is global, it is experienced differentially in various countries and locales around the world. Preventive measures such as lockdowns have a long history as non-pharmaceutical interventions to blunt the force of extreme mortality events. But there is, indeed, much that is new about the present COVID-19 crisis. This essay reflects on covert tyrannies underpinning the rationale for lockdowns, drawing on the case of Uganda. Drawing from both ethnographic fieldwork and secondary sources, I argue that the attendant mass surveillance and controls placed on human liberties in the context of a “war” against the new coronavirus—what I refer to as coronization of our lives—may surpass the tyranny experienced during the era of European colonization. Worse still, decision-making about the response to COVID-19 has, in the main, remained the exclusive preserve of state executives—governments at various levels, and some government-aligned epidemiologists, dovetailing nicely with military and security operatives—with little or no democratic oversight. At stake in this current dispensation of the ‘new normal’ is our survival as truly political beings.

E-Governance in the Posthuman World: A Case Study of ICDS-CAS Application
Abhijit Mitra, GC-178, Sector-III, Salt Lake City, Kolkata

The basic premise of this paper lies around how information and communication technology (ICT) has moulded the social-epistemic institutions and has changed the way we look at the world and deal with one another. Therefore, it calls for a re-examination of what is intrinsically human. This paper would study the framework for data protection and privacy in India in context to the e-Governance platform under the ICDS scheme from the lenses of STS. This study would analyse the impact of such platforms on beneficiaries (in identification, datafication etc.) and Anganwadi workers in their everyday work practices and its implications for citizenship from a group privacy perspective. This study will explore how the State can use/should use personal data in order to protect the fundamental rights of such workers for enabling a design justice paradigm. Using the Latourian Actor-network framework and empirical study, the paper would capture how the ICDS-CAS code anthropomorphises the workers day to day activities under the scheme ICDS. The empirical fieldwork data will help showcase how the artefact (ICDS-CAS app) is being inserted into the socio-materiality and is shaping up e-governance. The dimensions have changed from physical handling to digitization, addressing different problems and challenges but are still posed by technical limitations and non-error proof, which in turn influences the society. This study will explore how the State can use/should use personal data in order to protect the fundamental rights of such workers for enabling a design justice paradigm.

Visions of Global Transformation: Remaking environment and geopolitics with biological knowledge *Tess Doezema*

Visions of imminent environmental breakdown and corollary risks to human populations are pervasive in spaces of international diplomacy and cooperation, such as the OECD and the UN. Climate change, food security, and human health are widely treated in expert discourse as global problems that demand global solutions. Out of these assessments of such universally concerning risks has emerged a politics of global transformation that presents certain forms of cross-national cooperation and harmonization as objectively and scientifically necessary to sustain human life on earth. Such discourses seek to transcend national boundaries and appeal to basic human needs and interests at a global scale. And yet the mobilization of such projects of attempted global transformation inescapably take place in the context of histories of colonial violence and enduring asymmetries of power, wealth, and culpability for the very problems they set out to solve. This paper investigates the dynamics by which scientific knowledge and control of the biological world are imagined as novel agents of globalization, integrated in national policy discourses, and mobilized as catalysts for localized projects to reorder life and livelihoods. To this end, I examine bioeconomy projects and discourses produced within and across the United States and Brazil, both of which claim a leading role in the future “global bioeconomy.” In these spaces pursuant of global-scale objectivity, existing power relations are tested and reimagined, even as radical calls for the recognition of new rights and responsibilities are domesticated as stabilizing discourses for existing systems of global relationality.

“Worlding”, “Global Cities”, and the Impoverishment of the Right to the City *Stuart MacDonald, Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA); Govind Gopakumar, Concordia University*

Henri Lefebvre’s “right to the city” presents a discursive strategy towards resisting neoliberal policies in Global South cities. Yet this right has also been co-opted by purveyors and supporters of neoliberalism to pacify critics by conflating a right to existence within the city versus Lefebvre’s call for a right to agency in the decision making and transformation of the city from its current trajectory. Such a move, it is argued, embodies a “worlding” drive to corporatize “global cities” as market symbols to entice global capital. The paper will open by briefly contextualizing the semiotic nature of modernization as a means to accumulate and

centralize capital (especially via the “development discourse”), thereby contributing to capital flight and neocolonial hegemony. It will then explore what exactly a strong interpretation and implementation of Lefebvre’s right to the city entails, specifically for those particularly oppressed and ostracized by the global cities model—the urban poor. It argues for expanding informal networks and contingent projects in the Global South—strategic decentralization—maintaining (with Ananya Roy) that programs geared towards formalization of informal transactions under the guise of “modernity” further promote “global cities” oppression by emphasizing biopolitical governance and efficiency through technocratic “rational choice” policies that mask a shadow informality that further indentures classism and inequality. By advocating a “war on [socioeconomic] formality” within the Global South as a primary means to expand the right to the city, the paper questions whether STS should be situated within international formalization strategies such as the Sustainable Development Goals.

Session Organizers:

William Leeming, OCAD University

Ana Barahona, UNAM

115. (Re)configuring care practices in pandemic times IV

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Care practices were addressed in STS by Annemarie Mol (2002, 2008, 2010) as capturing a specific way of engaging with material reality as well as framing situated human relations. Hence, care bears not only upon intimacy or affectivity, but relates to forms of interdependency between ontology and normativity (“ontonorms”; Mol 2012). The session starts from and further develops the discussions on relevance of care practices focussing on the (re)configurations of care practices during the COVID-19 pandemic. Such a discussion of „care“ takes up not only a currently highly relevant social topic, but also acknowledges the salient empirical shaping of theoretical reflections on care in STS as ways of handling reality and transforming social relations. While COVID-19 differently addresses virologists, clinicians, physicists, epidemiologists, immunologists, or economics (Mol and Hardon 2020), a wide range of practices of care proliferated in response to the health crisis beyond these formal and mainstream settings, draw mainly on spatial (and social) proximity (neighbourhoods, peer-groups), and emphasised a temporal continuity of the caring engagement (regular visits, extended homeschooling). In a word: specific (re)configurations of care are rendered visible in dealing with personal concern, vulnerability, and (inter)dependence (Kittay 2015). The session includes contributions on: – expertise negotiated along care practices; – care related to groups traditionally framed as disadvantaged: elderly, people with disabilities, indigenous people, and other culturally diverse groups; – goods shaping actors understanding of care; – alliances of human and non-human entities as modes of pragmatic coping with pandemic crisis; – methodological adjustments regarding (re)configurations of care.

Participants:

Digitising practices of support in community mental health during Covid-19 *Ian Tucker, University of East London*

A digitisation of mental health support has been underway for some time (Ellis & Tucker, 2020). This includes the development of digital versions of existing practices of support, such as embedding existing therapeutic interventions in digital form (e.g. CBT), through to embracing digital ways of creating new forms of online-only support (e.g. peer support communities). These moves were underway pre-Covid, but the virus has catalysed a digitisation of support. Tens of thousands of ‘mental health apps’ are now available that range in focus from meditation through to AI-driven chatbots. There is also the use of digital platforms by existing community-based mental health groups, which can engage individuals with a range arts and creative activities, along with providing more general peer support. In this paper I explore new practices of support enacted in and through digital platforms. Several things are at stake relationally in new support

practices. The use of digital forms of support involves reconfiguring relations that individuals have with own mental health, with others, and with technologies. In person relationships of support (e.g. as featuring in peer-groups) face a simultaneous distancing (geometrically) and closeness (immediacy of digital support). Digital practices of support have the potential to transform the multiple spatial and temporal relations that constitute support, as technologies becomes relational actors in support 'in the present' that is shaped simultaneously with memories of the past and anticipations as to what the future holds. These questions shape the discussion in the present paper, which draws on a project investigating Covid-19 support practices in relation to community mental health groups in the UK that faced abruptly shifting their provision online as the pandemic struck. The paper presents insight of the reconfigured support practices and their impact on experiences of mental ill-health.

Olfactory Relations: Configuring a Neglected Sense of Care
Magdalena Eitenberger, University of Vienna, Department of Political Science; Antonia Modelhart, HCU - HafenCity University Hamburg; Lisa Wiedemann, Helmut Schmidt University Hamburg

Smelling as a sensory experience situates us directly within the environment and locates us in time and space. Memories, materials, danger, and environment: smelling is a practice of situating and relating. What happens when this taken-for-granted experience suddenly vanishes? One of the official COVID-19 symptoms is the loss of smell (anosmia). As a sign for the ongoing pandemic, anosmia stands in for the assumed temporality of an infectious disease as something that is transient. As a symptom, people losing their sense of smell has become a reliable harbinger, decrypting the onslaught of an enigmatic disease. But once it ceases to be a warning sign and its value is lost to the community, individuals are left uncared-for. In this paper, we ask in a lived and material sense what it means for people to live without olfactory relations. Since loss of sense of smell has not been consistently translated into medical-therapeutic practice, even fewer questions are asked about how care practices are shaped around this loss. Affected individuals have configured their own practices of care by connecting to others with similar experiences in online forums and through other digital means, creating care through connection. In our paper, we want to address these questions of translational work as well as practices of (self-)care that emerge out of losing the sense to smell. In so doing and in a larger sense, then, we also ask: how, as a society, may we care differently amidst a global pandemic?

Nursing Work in Pandemic Times: an ethnographic account of nurses' organizational work in COVID-19 care
Syb Kuijper, Erasmus School of Health Policy & Management; Martijn Felder, Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management; Iris Wallenburg, Institute for Health Policy and Management; Roland Bal, Erasmus University Rotterdam

More than ever before, Covid-care has raised the visibility of nurses' organisational work in healthcare organisations. Organising is an essential, yet often invisible, part of nursing work, which is rendered visible in nurses' creative and adaptive responses to the Covid pandemic. In this study, we focus on the organisational work of nurses in various roles and positions within healthcare organisations and analyse how nurses organisational work is informed by nursing expertise and shapes care at different interacting organisational levels. We build on literature that contends organizing as a natural part of nursing work, based on a combination of organising, practical and clinical knowledge (Allen, 2014). A blend of tacit and formal knowledge provides nurses with a high degree of organisational awareness, allowing them to place the organisation of care in broader, complex and dynamic organisational contexts (Endsley,

1995; Spitzer, 2015). Through ethnographic fieldwork, we studied nursing Covid-coordinators (in four hospitals) and interviewed nurses (N=20) in different hospitals and departments. We extend the literature of organisational work by revealing how nurses deploy an advanced and situated understanding of organisational contexts to mediate, integrate and organise care beyond bedside nursing (e.g. establishing crisis wards, oversee and foresee clinical processes and capacity, mobilizing and maintaining contact with different actors, management of equipment). This research contributes to a more layered understanding of nurses and nursing work, as well as to STS insights on the 'doings' of invisible and often marginalized groups of professional workers.

Session Organizer:

Stefan Nicolae, University of Trier

Discussant:

Cristina Popescu, EHESS - Centre d'Etude des Mouvements Sociaux

116. Legal Technologies: The Need For STS-Analyses - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Data-driven methods such as machine learning and artificial intelligence and their development for and deployment in a wide variety of social and societal contexts are currently experiencing a critical moment of academic, media and political discussion. This applies not least to the realm of law and legal practice: With applications such as forecasting court decisions via machine learning algorithms, automated reading, scanning and creation of legal texts, predictability of legal disputes, participatory tools for democratising legal practice comes the promise of innovation within the legal system. However, this innovation is not always welcomed enthusiastically and requires critical inquiry. An STS perspective is particularly fruitful in this realm when it comes to understanding the implementation dynamics and potential consequences of legal technologies. This open panel invites empirical and theoretical contributions that address the following questions and more: Which actors discuss legal technologies? Who benefits from the envisioned predictive power of machine learning? In what ways are legal practices and epistemologies shaped and reconceptualised by the application of data-driven methods? To what extent can legal technologies contribute to rethinking the relations between the individual and the legal apparatus and thereby contribute to "Good Relations"? Do the conceptual differences between a case-law system and a codified law system play a role in the question of compatibility with Big Data applications? To what extent is the potential of legal technologies overestimated and/or underestimated? How can law be rethought in light of data-driven methods? Is law facing an epistemological conflict between formalist and correlative approaches?

Participants:

Calculative Normativity Algorithms and Machine Learning as a Challenge for Legal Systems – A Media Sensitive Approach
Nikolaus Poehhacker, University of Graz

In the dominant understanding, legal practice is the interpretation and application of written or spoken rules – and thus, it is conceptualized as a Wittgenstein'ian language game. However, this perspective has been challenged by scholars (Vesting, 2015; Vismann, 2008), who are arguing that law is also media sensitive. This raises questions in terms of the ongoing digitization and algorithmization in relation to our legal systems. Drawing from my work on recommender systems developed by a public broadcaster, I will discuss how a German software development team tried to translate the ideal of diversity of news provision – as required by the German Constitutional Court – into a new recommender system. Through this I will illustrate the issues and challenges arising while translating legal norms into an algorithmic rationality, i.e., translating assessments of terms that are often qualitative and implicit, such as diversity, into algorithmic metrics. This is not only valuable in a perspective of algorithms under the rule of law, but also sheds light on digital

technologies as media within our legal systems, as law is not a mere system of symbols, but is mediated and thereby translated by the institutional and material setup enabling legal language (Jasanoff, 2011; Latour, 2009). In my contribution, I relate these approaches to my work on algorithmic normativity. Doing so, it enables us to explore how a media sensitive study of law can provide perspectives on the ongoing digitization of our legal systems, bridging insights from critical algorithm studies and STS perspectives on legal practices.

Making the Court Visible: Technological Requirements in the Construction of Brazilian Jurisprudence *Sara Munhoz, Universidade Federal de São Carlos (UFSCar)*

I aim to present the results of my PhD research on the disclosure system of Brazilian jurisprudence. Shaped by past decisions, the jurisprudence intends to project itself on similar future cases, imposing its interpretation. Although traditionally considered a civil law model, the Brazilian justice system has invested in valuing jurisprudence for its modernization and acceleration. Empirical research was carried out from a vast archive of technical-administrative documents from the Superior Court of Justice. The most modern Brazilian Court stands out as one of the most digitized courts worldwide since it receives, judges, and publishes all its cases digitally. Considerable efforts were made to implement Artificial Intelligence (AI) in classifying petitions, automated reading, minutes drafting, and disclosing judgments. Although still resistant to the idea of predictive justice, the automation of work routines and AI have been considered the only possible ways for a secure, swift, and, consequently, democratic justice system. Inspired by discussions on digital anthropology, STS, media studies, and governmentality debates, I describe how the concept of similarity, fundamental to the existence of jurisprudence, is operationalized in the Superior Court of Justice and how similarity is increasingly identified by and produced from a technical-mechanical apparatus for the storage, classification, and disclosure of judgments. In light of the above, public servants' technical work intertwined with computer applications transforms excessive data on published judgments into visible and, therefore, applicable jurisprudence.

DiGrenz – Potentials and Borders of Digitalization within Asylum Procedures *Angelika Adensamer, Vienna Centre for Societal Security; Antonia Csuk, University of Graz; Iris Eisenberger, University of Graz; Werner Fritz, FH Joanneum Graz; Annemarie Hofer, University of Graz; Marla Meilinger, University of Graz; Klaus Poier, University of Graz; Sandra Saywald-Wedl, University of Graz; Michaela Stangl, FH Joanneum Graz*

'DiGrenz – Potentials and Borders of Digitalization within Asylum Procedures' focuses on the question if and how asylum procedures can be improved by using digital technologies. The case study focuses on Austria, where several thousand asylum procedures are conducted every year. In the last year, over 60% of the decisions on the withdrawal of asylum recognition were proven to be incorrect. This is mainly due to the high number of cases and insufficient resources, leading to long procedures and flawed decisions, affecting the lives of thousands every year. To improve the procedures, digital technologies might be useful. One of these technologies in question is an AI-trained voice analysis tool, which can be used to assist in the determination of a person's country of origin. Another one is an app to improve communication between administration and asylum seekers, which is currently being developed. However, using digital technologies in the legal process raises important (fundamental) rights issues. This is especially true in asylum procedures, where a wrong decision – with or without the use of digital measures – may be life-threatening. This does not only imply legislative questions but requires an interdisciplinary approach. Taking into consideration STS perspectives, we therefore analyze the potentials and disadvantages of using digital technologies in

asylum procedures from a legal, technical, and sociological perspective, focusing on questions about the accessibility of legal procedures, using language as a prove of origin, assuring equality, and guaranteeing fundamental rights in a globally connected system.

The Materiality of Law: The Case of Online Dispute Resolution *Andrew Mamo, Northern Illinois University College of Law*

Online Dispute Resolution (ODR), the use of digital communications technologies, AI, and document management tools to assist in the resolution of disputes through mediation and arbitration (and, during the COVID-19 pandemic, even litigation), has been embraced by courts and administrative agencies to improve the efficiency of dispute resolution. It is prompting a rethinking of the nature of the courthouse more generally: from sites of formal state authority to “courts as a service.” The novelty of ODR platforms foregrounds the existence of the interface through which individuals access the law and become parties to legal proceedings. The design of ODR platforms is a provocation to examine not only the role of technology in forging new kinds of legal relationships, but also the materiality and situatedness of traditional mediation and arbitration practices. Mediation and arbitration occupy the periphery of legal theory despite their centrality to legal practice, a puzzle which Bruno Latour's analyses in *The Making of Law and Inquiry into Modes of Existence* help explain. By taking a practice-oriented view of the law and reorienting the study of mediation and arbitration around material practices, this study offers not only a critical analysis of how communications technology is interwoven into the fabric of individual disputes and the operations of the law, but also how contested meanings of “access to justice”—and of justice itself—shape the operations of these dispute resolution platforms.

Session Organizers:

Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld

Nikolaus Poehhacker, University of Graz

Chair:

Paola Lopez, University of Vienna

117. Teaching Science and Engineering for Social Justice – I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Science and engineering education bear significant responsibility in fostering democratic and just technoscientific practice, especially given the complicity of technoscience in several social injustices. For example, AI-based surveillance has reinforced the marginalization of minorities, while the use of toxic chemicals in the electronics industry has caused several worker miscarriages. However, pressured by a market-driven system that prioritizes technical skills, this responsibility is often relegated to ethics or STS courses that are separated from the core science/engineering curriculum. Further, as Dr. Timnit Gebru's recent exit from Google illustrates, the environments of professional technoscience are often themselves averse to critically analyzing issues of social justice and ethics in their practice. Consequently, science and engineering students seldom learn how to engage with social justice as it relates to the subject-matter and methods of technoscience. This is problematic as it can promote agnosticism or even antagonism towards considering the role of technoscience in perpetuating social injustices and inequity. How can we teach science/engineering for social justice in a system that often devalues social justice? In this panel, we invite submissions that critically engage with this question through theoretical and/or practical work. Examples include but are not limited to (re)designing and discussing: • Classroom strategies, courses, or curricula • Digital educational media such as games, simulations, and information visualizations • Policies and power dynamics of the educational system • Personal narratives as educators, administrators, or students as they relate to the challenges of teaching science/engineering for social justice.

Participants:

Educating the engineers we want to design our world *Ericka*

Johnson, Linköping University; Maria Eidenskog; Ola Leifler, Linköping University; Mikael Asplund, Linköping University

Engineering programmes should be in conversation with the needs of an unequal and uncertain world aching for responsible social change. As teachers and coordinators of a 5-year programme culminating in a Master's degree for IT professionals, we set out to make changes to our curriculum to equip graduates to contribute to such change. Taking the opportunity offered by a general programme makeover, we added three courses: "Law for IT and ethics", "Diversity and Gender in Application Development" and "IT for sustainability", which comprise 3 months' worth of studies in total and engage teachers and subject matter from outside the computer science department. Our aim was to broach gender and diversity issues as well as the relationship between IT, design, social structures, legal frameworks and power in the context of equitable and sustainable development. However, we are not sure these ideas actually diffuse into the academic culture students come into contact with and how they might impact students' perceptions of their education and dreams of their future role as engineers. So, we asked them. This paper reports the result: We analyse our own desires and reflections as well as the responses we have gathered from students, the programme committee, and teachers. Our analysis contextualises these results in conversations with recent ideas about data feminism (D'Ignazio & Klein 2019), sustainable design (Becker et al 2016; Allhutter 2012), STS in the development of a more sustainable engineering education (Pritchard & Baillie, 2006) and recent discussions of STS in education (Decuyper 2019).

Transdisciplinary collaborative teaching for tech justice *Isabelle Zaugg, Columbia University, Data Science Institute, Institute for Comparative Literature and Society*

With the help from a Collaboratory at Columbia Grant, two colleagues and myself developed the course "Multilingual Technologies and Language Justice" at Columbia University. The course bridges my own expertise in STS with the expertise of leading NLP researcher Smaranda Muresan and the renowned humanities scholarship of Lydia Liu. The course is transdisciplinary in its design and teaching, as well as in the student populations it serves; students range from graduates to undergraduates and bring a mix of backgrounds in computational skills, humanities, and the social sciences. The course is designed to give students a historical, political, and ethical foundation for understanding the genesis and impact of language tech, and especially the many gaps for digitally-disadvantaged language speakers from minoritized and Indigenous language communities. But it doesn't stop there – our course helps students build NLP skill sets through project-based learning, pushing them to find solutions for the challenges they have identified. Student projects have ranged from The Columbia Language Perspectives Project (which recently won top place in Columbia's inaugural "Best Student Data Science Course Project Competition"), to a COVID-related sentiment/issue analysis of New York City-based minority-language tweets, to an e-Learning app for learning the Shipibo-Conibo language, an Indigenous language of South America. This talk shares best practices in transdisciplinary collaborative teaching as an effective and engaging way to embed ethics and justice concerns within technical domains.

Peace engineering as an emergency in engineering education: A speculative approach for Colombia *Juan David Reina Rozo*
Peace has been a disputed concept in educational agendas worldwide. Since the Peace Accord signed between the former guerrilla FARC-EP and the Colombian Government in 2016, this term was politicized inside Universities. The National University of Colombia is the biggest public university, having nine campuses across the country. This institution had an important

role in the negotiation process of the Peace Accord and in its implementation. At the educational level, the accord allows the creation of Peace Courses in schools and universities. But, the questions that emerge are how will it look like a peace course for engineering? Follow by, what perspective(s) and discussion(s) will be present at the course? These questions are important in a context characterized by the elimination in 2020 of an STS course at the Engineering School called Ingenuity, Science, Technology, and Society (ISTS). ISTS was offered as an elective course for students of all undergraduate programs at Bogotá Campus, with content guided by the engaged engineering praxis. Taking into account the limitations inside the institution due to the political environment to foster the idea of a peace engineering course, new strategies have to be created related to social justice, solidarity, peace, and critical thinking of future engineers practice in one of the most inequality countries in the world. Finally, a preliminary open proposal of its new elements, methodologies, and contents is presented to continue a collective dialogue towards more critical technoscientific disciplines that assume and reflect on its ties with war, inequality, and exclusion.

Engineering Education, a Curriculum Overview for Social Justice: Case Study of ReCIDS *Juan Sebastian Rincón Bucheli, ReCIDS, Pacific node; Carolina Salcedo Portilla, Universidad del Valle; Sandra Milena Bonilla Cely, ReCIDS, Andean node; Armando Jose Vargas Salcedo, ReCIDS, Pacific node*

The world's predominant economic development system based on the distribution of wealth keeps countries in search of utopia progress; such is the case of Latin America where the social panorama has been the same for more than a century, highlighting the increase in poverty, inequality, unemployment, and injustices within the social, economic and environmental dimensions. Faced with this frame of reference, academics and thinkers have chosen to enhance collaborative work and networking, such is the case of the Colombian Network of Engineering and Social Development - ReCIDS, which identifies the importance of establishing a platform for the analysis and reflection regarding the responsibility of engineering education and its role in the complexities and social realities of the territories. Thus, this network proposes to explore and review the history of conventional engineering education, its curricular programs, and learning methodologies, to advocate for the application of engineering for social justice. With this in mind, the proposal shows in an exploratory manner the main characteristics of engineering education and the experiences, analysis, and proposals from the point of view, perspectives, and narratives of various academic stakeholders from different public and private universities in Colombia through a qualitative methodology using semi-structured interviews. Finally, based on these inputs, it is expected to promote curriculum construction according to the social environment and its multiple realities for its analysis from the engineering point of view.

Session Organizer:

Aditya Anupam, Georgia Institute Of Technology

118. Economization of the inpatient health care sector and its effects on knowledge translation, innovation, professions and working conditions

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

One explanation for the fragile state of hospital sectors around the world during the COVID-19 pandemic can be assumed in the diffusion of economization efforts. The financialization of medical care created organizational weak points: work intensification, bureaucratization and increasing managerial control led to an exhausted work force and an economy of scarcity. However, different groups of hospital staff are affected differently: Physicians, clinical scientists, biomedical researchers, (study) nurses and management – among others – are each characterized by

specific professional tasks like medical treatment, research or management. We want to understand, how do they cope with the changed organizational setting and its inherent contradictions? Do new tasks, career patterns or professions emerge as a result? Furthermore, do the organizational changes of inpatient health care also affect the conditions for knowledge translation? Finally, what are the compounding effects of the external shock of the Covid-19-pandemic and economization efforts on the organization of inpatient health care? We invite empirical and theoretical papers discussing these and related research questions: • How is health care staff affected in its daily practice by the organizational change due to economization efforts? • What kind of behavior is developed to cope with altered framework conditions? • Does the financialization of health care change the organizational conditions for professional knowledge translation? • How is the financialization of health care affecting the response to the COVID-19-pandemic? • To what extent does financialization influence innovation? By answering these research questions, the panel contributes to ongoing STS debates on the complex interrelation of healthcare, (medical) translation and financialization.

Participants:

A Bespoke Workforce for the Bioeconomy: The Evolution of the Clinical Research Practitioner in the United Kingdom
Rachel Faulkner-Gurstein, King's College London

One form that the economisation of health has taken in the United Kingdom is the rise of the research agenda, where the National Health Service (NHS) is increasingly expected to generate medical and economic benefits through clinical research. The rise of research has seen the emergence of a new specialist workforce located within the NHS known as Clinical Research Practitioners (CRPs). Drawing on interviews and survey data conducted in 2021 within one of the UK's largest and most research-active hospitals, this paper explores the rise and professionalisation of the CRP workforce. CRPs are specialists in clinical research; patient care is not within their professional role. Yet in practice, for CRPs the boundaries between research and care are not well defined. During the pandemic, they were explicitly called upon as a reserve army of health care workers. Understanding how CRPs navigate thorny professional dilemmas of care work and knowledge work can help us better understand the embodied skills that contribute to clinical knowledge production, as well as help shed light on new forms of labour emerging as a result of recent transformations of the health system.

Economization and Confusion: Sexual and Reproductive Health Care During New York State's First Surge of COVID-19
Rajani Bhatta, University at Albany, SUNY; Elise Andaya, Department of Anthropology, University at Albany

This paper seeks to elucidate the impact of COVID-19 on working conditions, daily work patterns, and the scope of work of frontline providers who serve minority populations during the "first surge" of COVID-19 in New York State. We draw from interview material with nineteen frontline sexual and reproductive (SRH) health providers including midwives, doulas, OB/GYNs, lactation consultants, and labor and delivery nurses serving racial and ethnic minority populations about their experience with provision of and adaptations to care from March to October 2020. Lack of coordination and communication at different levels: between the state and New York City; between hospitals; between hospitals and local health departments, and; between hospital administrators and frontline providers produced widespread confusion about safety protocols and clinical policies and increased fear and anxiety for both patients and providers. Insufficient infrastructural investment for personal protective equipment (PPE), COVID testing, and pivot to telehealth in public hospitals and clinics led to negative working conditions including overwork, burnout, and exposure to emotionally traumatic scenes/situations. The confusion and chaos experienced by providers reflected and amplified the effects of preexisting resource inequities and longer existing forms of economization in

the health sector, including decades of cuts to public facilities, closures of hospitals, and the emergence of "maternity care deserts." Asking whether an ethics of care and good relations can be practiced under such extremely challenging circumstances, the research nonetheless notes numerous and creative initiatives by individuals and institutions to produce evidence-based guidance, ensure continuity of care, and deliver timely and compassionate care.

Anticipatory Work: Prognostic Assessment, Clinical Communication and Care-planning of The Palliative Care Team
Anne-chie Wang

How does the palliative care team cope with the uncertainty in end-of-life care? This paper adopts the concept of "anticipatory work" to explore the care work in prognosis, involving forecast knowledge, sentimental values, and future-coordination activities. Data include in-depth interviews of caregivers and medical professionals and participant observation in a medical center for twelve months. This paper found that the palliative care team addresses the prognosis in end-of-life care to foresee the dying trajectory rather than the recovery time. While the palliative care team develops a prognosis, they use evidence-based information and interactive cues to make predictions. By clinical communication, the palliative care team foretells a patient's survival time and probes the patient and family members' expectations toward end-of-life care. As coordinating with the future-oriented care plan, the palliative care team approaches three kinds of time frames: patient survival time, patient's life trajectory, and hospital regulation, which separately represent the clinical, social, and institutional time frame. This paper reveals that the palliative care team manages the uncertainty in end-of-life care by anticipating the patient's future time frame and managing the patient and family caregivers' expectations.

Metamorphoses – Reconstructing The Imprint Of Socio-Technical Evolution On Medical Prescriptions
Stefan Schellhammer, University of Münster; Meral Avci, RWTH Aachen University; Patrick Troglauer, University Münster; Kerstin Grothusheitkamp, University of Marburg

Medical prescriptions represent a unique artefact for historic analyses on the evolution of modern healthcare systems. While current debates center on the digitalization of this artefact, it is worth noting that it carries a century-long history of supporting and structuring communication in healthcare. Since the separation of doctors and pharmacists required communication between the two to be documented, this artefact became central to organizing, governing and structuring the provision of healthcare. This paper reports on the methodological challenges in exploring and analyzing one of the largest collections of historical medical prescriptions covering a time period of 300 years. These historical artefacts are imprinted by the socio-technical context of the time exemplified by reordering, formalizing and standardizing the information it carries. Over time their appearance changed, adapting the artefact to the needs of the emerging healthcare system. Our analysis allows for reconstructing central parts which remain relevant for the design of ehealth infrastructures. So far, we identified three metamorphoses: First, we show how the artefact transformed from a rather simple communication device to a legally binding certificate. Second, the artefact documents the emergence of reimbursement as a new way of organizing financial flows. Finally, the prescription morphed into a standardized artefact optimized for machine-readability in a response to being a mass-phenomenon. Our contribution is twofold: Methodologically, we discuss the challenge of tracing an artefact throughout time. On a theoretical level, we introduce the notion of metamorphosis as a way to account for the changing nature of prescriptions throughout time.

Then, Now, And Hereafter: Changing Perceptions Of

Technology Innovation *Meral Avci, RWTH Aachen University; Kerstin Grothusheitkamp, University of Marburg; Stefan Schellhammer, University of Münster; Patrick Troglauer, University Münster*

In Germany, as in many other countries, innovations in healthcare and particular electronic prescriptions remain challenging. Two cases of such innovation processes serve as the empirical basis of this paper. The so-called "Muster 16" represents the first official, standardized, and machine-readable form for prescriptions. It is the result of an innovation process starting locally in Munich during the 1960s due to the institutionalization of the prescription clearinghouse that shortly after proliferated throughout the entire German healthcare system. Although this innovation arose out of a problem faced by pharmacists, they were able to convince physicians and health insurances of their innovation. A collaborative approach was essential as the resulting changes affected also their practices. The second case concerns the ongoing struggle of policymakers to introduce electronic prescriptions nationwide for over one decade. Both innovations are comparable in their scope. Our paper starts with the observation of a striking difference in the way pharmacists, physicians, and health insurances engaged in collaboration in the former case and the inability to create common interests in the latter. Our comparative case study traces the different perceptions of the actors in each case to answer the research question "How and why technology innovations can be perceived differently?". We find the starkest contrast in the way policymakers are involved and innovations were linked to the concerns of daily practitioners. By examining both cases, we explore the necessity of innovations to address everyday practices and, therefore, contribute to a better understanding of the acceptance of technology innovations.

Session Organizer:

Barbara Hendriks, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin and German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies

Discussant:

Sebastian Starystach, Charité - Universitätsmedizin Berlin

119. Oceans of Abundance? Biomaterial Extraction between Ecological & Human Health

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Ocean life figures centrally in competing narratives of marine futures. Conservation policy and environmentalists describe marine organisms as vulnerable victims, devastated by over-production. Meanwhile, Blue Economy policies are reimagining marine life as a key resource for biomaterial extraction. In the biomedical arm of the Blue Economy, the abundant potentials of marine biomaterials are pursued in combination with human bodies to innovate a more healthful (human) future. Across pharmaceutical, biotech, and material technology sectors, marine life often appears, as Stefan Helmreich (2007) has written, as "endlessly generative" and "overflowing with (re)productivity." This session will explore conceptual and visual resources for the study of marine organisms at the intersection of environmental and human health. The papers in the session follow marine organisms and their biomaterials as move within and through different--and at times contradictory--epistemological, legal, and bio-ecological pathways. As nascent bioscientific interventions intensify the role of humans in planetary functions, we investigate how they engender, as Jason Moore (2015) writes, "denser, more geographically expansive, and more intimate" relations among humans and nonhumans. Between these futures of imagined good health and over-exploited oceans, we ask: For whom do these entangled networks constitute "good" or "bad" relations of abundance?

Participants:

Circulatory Systems: Horseshoe crabs, ocean ecologies, and biomedicine *Kristoffer Whitney, Rochester Institute of*

Technology

In 1983, the U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) mandated that all intravenous pharmaceuticals, surgical tools, and implants undergo the Limulus Amoebocyte Lysate (LAL) test to detect the presence of endotoxins. Since, the LAL test has become the global standard for endotoxin detection in the biopharmaceutical industry. Lysate is derived from the blue blood of horseshoe crabs. The horseshoe crab's now crucial role in the security of human health networks have made it a highly valued resource (one quart of blood costs approximately \$15,000 USD). While crab bleeding is nonlethal, a growing number of ecologists are concerned that the industry suppresses morbidity rates among bled crabs, damaging population numbers and regional ocean ecologies. This places ecological and human health in tension. This paper explores the discursive, epistemological, and ontological tensions between horseshoe crabs as ocean and estuary denizens, objects of conservation, sources of economic livelihoods, and protectors of human health. Following the circulation of horseshoe crabs and the biomaterials extracted from them, I explore the rhetoric and knowledge produced by stakeholders in struggles over the fate of these creatures. In the process, I trace the divergent ontologies brought into being by the politics of crab harvest and conservation: the robust populations and ecosystems that fishers and pharmaceutical companies claim horseshoe crabs represent, versus these same species cast as symbols of fragile ocean ecologies on the verge of collapse by conservationists. These wildly different natures and narratives offer a case study in the seemingly intractable 'ontological politics' of marine extraction and governance.

The sky's the limit? Boundless visions of shrimp-shell waste futures *Hannah Dickinson, Durham University*

Six-eight million metric tons of shellfish waste is estimated to be produced annually. Shrimp shells form a significant component of this shellfish waste due to growing global levels of shrimp consumption, wild harvest, and aquaculture production as well as the fact that around 45-48% of shrimp raw material is discarded as waste. The improper disposal of shrimp-shell waste is recognised as a significant environmental problem that demands innovative solutions. Identifying novel ways of utilising rather than discarding shrimp-shells has become a key focus of research in the biosciences and figures prominently in biotechnological visions espoused by proponents of a circular blue economy. This drive to make use of shrimp waste has been enlivened by a developing fascination with the manifold potentials of chitosan - a biomaterial extracted from the shells of crustacean. Chitosan is heralded as the panacea for a seemingly endless range of socio-ecological ills, ranging from the mundane to the mind-boggling. Already operating as a key component of products used in textiles, waste-water, agriculture and food industries; chitosan is also positioned as a remedy to humanity's reliance on petroleum-based plastics. Further, chitosan is poised to enable the longevity of human-life on earth and beyond: with researchers exploring how chitosan can ensure survival on the battlefield, beat cancers, and build settlements on Mars. This paper will explore the boundless visions of chitosan applications, and analyse how these visions are brought back down to earth by financial, legal, and political structures which variably foster and curtail the global circulations of this biomaterial.

Consuming the Future: Jellyfish Blooms and Endless Life *Elizabeth R Johnson, Durham University*

Fueled by fears of destroyed fisheries, ruined livelihoods and famine, jellyfish blooms are considered an ecological threat in their over-abundance. Scientists suggest that the blooms are indicative of a syndrome of ecological stressors caused by commercial shipping and over fishing. As part of efforts to combat burgeoning jellyfish populations, researcher and policy makers in the EU are coming together to reimagine jellyfish as a "food of the future." Rather than "trash animal," they are poised to become a low calorie, low fat, and B12-rich "sustainable

protein", thus becoming a "mainstream solution to the unprecedented depletion of the oceans" (Saibante 2015). Alongside those efforts to expand consumption, jellyfish proteins have grown increasingly central in laboratories in the fields of biosensing and biotech: the Green Fluorescent Proteins of *Aequorea victoria* have been incorporated into a system of biological surveillance in hospitals, laboratories, and field sites; scientists are studying jellyfish and hydra stem cells to solve a range of health issues; and material scientists have turned to jellyfish mucus to solve the problem of marine micro-plastic pollution. Jellyfish bodies, therefore, are simultaneously viewed as a threat to human life and a promise for healthier more abundant human futures. This paper will explore these efforts to unite regional marine ecology management with culinary and biomaterial innovation. In it, I examine what is at stake in how marine ecology and biomedical industries differentially understand the overflowing reproductive capacities of jellyfish bodies.

Surfing the In-Betweens: Methods of an Impossible Practice
Helen J. Bullard, Milwaukee Institute of Art and Design

Navigating the methodological and reflexive spaces between interdisciplinary collaborators relies upon a strong sense of their mutual spaces of production. And when those collaborators bring with them their animals and other research subjects, their lived experiences and ethics, their tried and tested methods as well as an openness to experiment and new perspectives, those spaces of production can unfurl into infinitely unanticipated territories. This creative presentation will focus on the developing work of four collaborators and their in-betweens: spaces, species, disciplines, methods and stories. Their good relations, their mutual spaces of production, the circulation of biomaterials, policies and papers, speculative futures and the slippages between methodological approaches. Stories can, as Thom Van Dooren suggests, "hold open simultaneously a range of points of view, interpretations, temporalities, and possibilities" (2014). In this story, I explore the (im)possible practice of surfing the in-betweens from the perspective of an interdisciplinary artist with a long-standing interest in art-(social) science collaboration and environmental change.

Session Organizer:

Elizabeth R Johnson, Durham University

Discussant:

Nicole C Nelson, University of Wisconsin Madison

120. Imagining precision agriculture for food system sustainability

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Participants:

Make bloom and let wither: Biopolitics of precision agriculture at the dawn of surveillance capitalism *Ryan Stock, Northern Michigan University; Maaz Gardezi, Virginia Tech*

Precision agriculture is an assemblage of data-driven agricultural technologies, discursively articulated as a clever gambit against climate-induced food insecurity. Agritech companies engage in data grabbing as an accumulation strategy and to influence farmers' behaviors, opening agrarian frontiers for surveillance capitalism. Wielding big data to manage and optimize species within food production systems becomes a biopolitical calculation of "make bloom and let wither," with implications for the agrarian question of labor. Drawing on mixed methods fieldwork from South Dakota and Vermont, we document how different actors perform and contest agri-algorithmic subjectivities, producing novel terrains of food politics and neoliberal state-citizen relations.

Agri-Food Automation and Surveillance & Greenhouse Migrant Labour in Southwestern Ontario *Olivia Doggett, Faculty of*

Information, University of Toronto

Agricultural automation and surveillance technologies such as precision agriculture (PA) and farming robots are increasingly considered and adopted by agri-food practitioners in Canada. Promising reduced labour costs, healthier food, more efficient and environmentally sustainable farm management and production, these purported benefits exclude any consideration for existing agricultural labour practices. This exclusion matters because in Canada, temporary or seasonal agricultural programs classify workers as temporary, non-citizen and low-skilled meaning workers often face deep-seated racial and economic inequalities. Seasonal migrant workers make up the majority of Canada's agricultural processing and packaging workforce and some have already experienced the impact of emerging agri-tech. Automation has cut greenhouse jobs in half at some Canadian farms and surveillance technologies are beginning to be employed to control workers' pace and production levels. Furthermore, workers report that these new technologies often make mistakes or miscalculations or work too slowly, which can be very stressful as while "robots cannot be penalized for their slow pace, agricultural workers can." This ethnographic study investigates the impacts that emerging agri-food technologies have on migrant greenhouse labour practices in southwestern Ontario, Canada. Through semi-structured interviews with migrant farm workers, greenhouse farmers and agri-food tech representatives and on-site visits to greenhouses, this research evaluates how agri-food technologies affect the social and hierarchical nature of relationships and labour processes in the greenhouse as well as how these technologies are designed to participate in existing agricultural labour practices.

Make it precise, make it visible: the digital transformations of Brazilian agribusiness. *Evandro Smarieri, State University of Campinas - UNICAMP*

This work presents partial results of an ongoing research on the process of introduction of information technologies to the agricultural industry in Brazil, especially in the cultivation of sugar cane. Within a proposal linked to sociological studies of science and technology, this work carries an approach inspired by the actor-network theory, as developed by Bruno Latour, Michel Callon, John Law and Annemarie Mol, but also, strongly interested by works about sciences practices in Donna Haraway, Isabelle Stengers Natasha Myers, and especially in the philosophy of individuation of Gilbert Simondon. With a perspective based on this theoretical and methodological basis, we start from the recent history of digital agriculture in Brazil, dealing particularly with the concept of Precision Agriculture. Beyond the historical register of this process, the investigative work bears other three axes: first, a reflection on the word "precision", taken as a trope, that is, a word that carries specific narratives; second, we explore the materially heterogeneous network that supposedly gives more "precision" to agricultural industry. To do that, we give an special framing on "technical images" and the use of multispectral images, which condenses data obtained by cameras and other sensors, we argue that these images create a vision, through technical mediation, that recursively transforms reality, either in the work of engineers, in the laboratory, and on the use at field on farms; finally, we aim to define the specificities of Brazilian Precision Agriculture and compare it with the development of this trend abroad.

Impact of Scientific and Tacit Knowledge on Precision Agriculture and Greenhouse Operations in Turkey *Serra Baykal*

Precision agriculture is vital for ensuring sustainable agriculture, especially in greenhouse cultivation. Yet, understanding and applying precision agriculture requires both technical skills and infrastructure. While scientific and engineering aspects of precision agriculture are covering an important part of literature, STS studies are focusing on enabling factors, innovation system

components, and best-applicable strategies to diffuse necessary technologies. In that framework, this paper investigates the impact of scientific and tacit knowledge on Turkish greenhouse owners to change traditional production methods towards precision agriculture practices. Qualitative research methods are used in this paper. We conducted semi-structured interviews with greenhouse owners and surveys with public servants working as agricultural consultants. Research context is designed to understand sources of knowledge, information networks, balance between theoretical and practical knowledge, and impact of tacit knowledge towards precision agriculture practices. This paper contributes to STS studies in three ways. First, this is currently among the first academic studies in Turkey for knowledge development and diffusion factors in greenhouse operations, favoring precision agriculture. Second, this paper elaborates precision agriculture through innovation system approach and technology diffusion factors underneath STS literature. Third, the main focus is given to an interdisciplinary STS area, interlinking the influence of knowledge under innovation system approach, potential of greenhouse operations in Turkey in applying precision agriculture, and factors leading to lock-in to traditional methods, instead of adopting existing scientific, technological and engineering solutions.

Envisioning the role of precision agriculture in food system sustainability transitions *Maaz Gardezi, Virginia Tech; Ayorinde Ogunyiola, South Dakota State University; Asim Zia, University of Vermont*

Proponents of precision agriculture (PA) hope that the widespread collection of big data, improvements in computational power and algorithmic capacity will bring sustainability to agricultural systems. Here, we explore how actors across the food system value chain envision sustainability transitions through PA. We conceptually integrate the multi-level perspective with the critical social science scholarship on PA to situate sustainability transitions research within a broader political economy of agriculture. By utilizing empirical data collected from anticipatory approaches, such as foresight in the US, this paper shows that although PA can reconcile some of the demands for environmental and economic sustainability in agriculture, the road to enhancing social and ethical sustainability is fraught with uncertainties relating to the expectations of benefits and risks of PA, the ambiguities of governing these technologies, and the promises and perils of technologies to tackle some of the most serious issues pertaining to climate change.

Session Organizer:

Maaz Gardezi, Virginia Tech

121. Role of Science, Technology and Innovation in Post-Covid

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

The world is dealing with one of the most challenging periods in modern times, it is evident that Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) is the key to providing critical and indispensable tools to help overcome the current situation. The transfer of knowledge, skills and solutions in the science and technology fields can have a profound and lasting impact on society. The COVID-19 pandemic has underscored the pressing need for countries to focus more on elevating science, technology and innovation (STI) in both policy and practical terms. But the coronavirus pandemic also drives leaders to ensure that the development benefits of STI translate directly into the daily lives of people all over the world. We need more research, collaboration, data and knowledge sharing to cope with the immediate impacts of the coronavirus crisis and go beyond it. More than ever, we need a multilateral approach to ensuring the STI serves both strategic and development ends. The initiative aims at making a substantive contribution to addressing the different sectoral challenges associated with and responding to lessons learned from the COVID-19 pandemic by looking into how innovations and technologies can help various sectors like energy, agriculture and education respond to similar challenges in the

future and how to enable life-long learning with digital tools that are fit for purpose.

Participants:

Exploring Patterns of Regional Trade and International Cooperation in the Caribbean Community: A System of Innovation Perspective *Vairaj Arjune, Centre for Studies in Science Policy, Jawaharlal Nehru University; Rajbeer Singh, Assistant Professor at Centre for Studies in Science Policies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*

This paper focus on developing countries of the Caribbean, particularly, the fifteen member countries of the Caribbean Community. With more than four decades in operation, numerous challenges to economic development confront the Caribbean countries - the deterioration of trade preferences and the imposition of the World Trade Organization (WTO) system. The lack of progress in implementing CARICOM policies and structural factors, particularly the similarities in economies, are seen as factors inhibiting the growth of the region. Thus, the effects of contemporary globalization and rapid development of industrializing countries have altered the trajectory of CARICOM developmental priorities. These trends are most visible in the declining importance of trade preferences with the EU and the United States. At the same time, intraregional CARICOM knowledge exchange shows little promise for growth while Latin America and Asia are emerging as an increasingly important knowledge partners in the future. With CARICOM now harnessing the potential of Science, Technology, and Innovation (STI) capabilities by acquiring basic S&T infrastructure and manpower, they will need to open to global markets and trends, be prepared to absorb cultural shock, and to be innovative in creating strategic alliances. From this perspective, it is important for science policy scholars to analyse Science and Technology (S&T) instruments through which governments are piloting international collaborations and communicative relationships with scientists in establishing regional blocs, global partnerships with MNCs, and university-industry relationships. The study brings together analytical framework in innovation systems with empirical evidence from the Caribbean Community. The study attempts to build on other studies that have elaborated in regionalism in the Community and adds the perspective of science and technology as the primary frontier for the societal and economic development of the region.

2) Analyzing Innovation Governance under Science and Technology Policy in India *Krishna Tripathi, Centre for Studies in Science policy, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi; Rajbeer Singh, Assistant Professor at Centre for Studies in Science Policies, Jawaharlal Nehru University, India*

Policy making is based on political enterprise. It imparts the governing elements with guiding principles in democratic setups. Since the dawn of policy making on science and technology in India, the focus has been on addressing existing challenges pertaining to scientific development. Policy formulation has undergone a sea change in terms of its focus since 1958 to STI policy 2013. The existing STIP 2013 was brought in to bridge the gaps left by earlier policies and to communicate effectively to the globalised process of innovation. It has taken a far more integrated and comprehensive outlook and has brought the issues of society, inclusive growth and accountability into its ambit by recognising it as a crucial component of national science policy governance. Governing innovation under the ambit of STI policy however has proven rather challenging, given its idea of inclusivity regarding innovations. Specifically hurdles are posed by novel and newly emerging innovations which are various associated risks and uncertainties. Hence the question here is that how the emerging innovation could be governed in this scenario. The present paper explores this question by using Responsible Innovation (RI) approach. The RI approach, among the most

exhaustive of the innovation approach, not only presents how to innovate but also provides governance solutions by incorporating deliberation and participation dimensions in the innovation process, hence facilitating effective implementation of the STI policy in India. The paper concludes that involvement of all the relevant stakeholders in the STI policy machinery along with their active participation is significant for governing of the newly emerging innovations.

3) Role of Women's Scientists in Indian Science: a case Study of Selected Physical Science Institutions *Kuldeep Minda, Centre for Studies in Science Policy, Jawaharlal Nehru University*

Till date, science as a career for women's scientist has always been a difficult choice them. To encourage women scientists and to inspire girls to take up science as a career we need special programs and policies. We also need to understand their current status in science and what contribution they make for Indian science. There is no proper assessment of their current status in science. Specially in Physical Science, there is also challenges to explore, the contribution of women scientist to in Indian science arena, Based on literature review and talking with experts in this area focus of study is at what extent contribution of women's work recognized and how their research productivity considered in compare to their counterpart. Another problem is how women's scientist work comes under come under so called "glass ceiling effect". Further to this problem, is the challenge to explore how can women overcome this effect? Hierarchy and gender stereotyping get penetrated into equality pattern and convert into strong "glass ceiling effect" for women's scientist works. In my research, I have first of all select five central universities physics department, based on their "NIRF Ranking" five CSIR-laboratories, or three autonomous research institutes based on their research productivity. After doing much exercise on the data, quantitative analysis was carried out to show that how women scientists in physics discipline has average representation with great achievement. The area of physics is considered a tough science for women but trends of research productivity in the concern discipline show that contribution from women scientist is a not less than comparison with men scientist.

STI in Indian Education after Post-Covid *Dinesh Gupta, Dharm Samaj College, Aligarh*

Science, technology and innovation (STI) have played a key role in responding to the COVID-19 pandemic and the unprecedented psychosocial effects. STI has played a key role during lockdown either an employee was working from home (WFH) or the students were studying at home (SAH) and also for the essential services technology helped alot. We discuss whether the amount of digital communication technology use for virtual meetings during the lockdown promoted the perception of social support. The research findings indicates that the amount of digital technology use reduced feelings of loneliness, anger/irritability, and boredom and increased belongingness via the perception of social support. A growing number of scientists points out that the problem of digital technology overuse has direct adverse consequences (e.g. by consumption of violent media content, experiencing of cyberbullying or negative affect often accompanying excessive usage), the often neglected indirect media effects should not be overseen. It was also found that during the COVID-19 pandemic, in some households children likely also witnessed or experienced more violence due to digital overuse. The study tries to discuss the mixed effects of STI (Science, Technology and Innovation)

Session Organizer:

Pradeep Kumar, Department of Education, Associate Professor, Dharm Samaj College, Aligarh

Discussant:

Ashutosh Tiwari, Centre for Studies in Science Policy,

Jawaharlal Nehru University

122. Nudging/Libertarian Paternalism Open Panel

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

An open panel to discuss theories and practices of "nudging" (also referred to as "libertarian paternalism") as a way to respond to unequal and uncertain worlds. Open panel to function in round robin format between paper presenters, with brief Q&A following each paper and wider discussion to follow all presentations and their corresponding Q&A sessions. Cass R. Sunstein (2014) defines nudges as "liberty-preserving approaches that steer people in particular directions, but that also allow them to go their own way," and they are "intended to ensure that people do not struggle when they seek to interact with their government or to achieve their goals." This open panel will address questions of nudging's efficacy with regard to rationality, ethics, and agency within unequal and uncertain worlds. Can nudging prove to instantiate greater equality and certainty when we most need it, and if so, how?

Participants:

A Justification Paradox for Libertarian Paternalism *Andrew Buzzell, York University, Toronto*

Nudges, the instruments of libertarian paternalism, rely on specific cognitive conditions both to be effective and to support their mode of justification. They are often used for epistemic ends as well, targeting distinctively cognitive or epistemic improvements - an instance of what has been described as epistemic paternalism. There is a problematic feedback loop between the poor health of an epistemic environment, the ensuing justification to intervene, and the increasing difficulty in crafting an intervention within this scope of justification that we can reasonably expect to be effective. In a polluted epistemic environment, interventions designed to improve it are often faced with a justificatory paradox. We paternalistically interfere because the polluted epistemic environments impairs our epistemic efforts, but this very pollution raises the stakes in terms of the degree of interference required to achieve successful outcomes. The justification for nudges is in part based on the extent to which they fly under the radar of strong preferences. If changes in the epistemic environment shift preferences, we have to abandon the objective or license further encroachments on autonomy. This reveals an underlying tension - either the justification to nudge also justifies more coercive intervention, or, that we were justified to nudge was in some way accidental - it just happened to be the case that the desired epistemic outcome could be achieved without resistance. I argue that there is a dependence between the health of the epistemic environment and the feasibility of deploying justifiable epistemic interventions.

Unlocked Agency: Transhuman Nudging for the Posthuman Age *Daniel Shussett, Villanova University*

This paper begins with an examination of traditionally conceived human agency from Aristotle to now (represented by Bruce Sterling), read in the context of futuristic fears. We then learn, from Tillman Vierkant, Fabio Paglieri, and Joseph Heath and Joel Anderson, that traditional human agents are woefully lacking in willpower, although this can be strengthened by external mechanisms. F. Allan Hanson and Polycarp Ikuenobe deepen our understanding of the social mechanisms that alter the traditional picture of human agency, and Andy Clark and Lambros Malafouris deepen our understanding of material mechanisms. The combination of these lines of thought leads us to the public policy concept of 'nudging'. Following an exploration of nudging, we consider how social-material environment manipulations affect our rationality, ethics, and agency. Accordingly, we then consider how nudges may respond to agential concerns in light of science-fiction transhuman augmentation, and also if we can consider this sort of human enhancement as nudging.

Session Organizer:

Daniel Shussett, Villanova University

123. Shaping AI: Who's afraid of big methodological, historical, political questions?

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

Artificial intelligence presents an area of research and innovation in which relations between science and society, and between the technical and the social, are today undergoing re-articulation in several different dimensions. On the methodological level, the rise of new forms of machine learning has opened up possibilities for pragmatist, contextual models of communication - and associated epistemologies - to find uptake in the formerly "closed world" of computational sciences. On the historical level, the internalist (as well as popular) depiction of AI as the next revolution raises the question of whether and how AI today presents a form of revolutionary science. Not only do geo-political framings of a global "AI race" make for a striking contrast with Kuhnian revolutions, such as relativity theory, and with more recent, "post-political" revolutions such as genetics. In relation to AI, it may not take us very far to proclaim, once more, our skepticism about the capacity of science to unleash revolution on society. Finally, we may be forced to come to terms with the fact that AI is inherently participatory. As it builds on platforms for data capture and dynamic feedback, today's AI is only as capable as the personal, real-world data and actions on which it feeds. It is also notoriously racist. What does it mean to call for democratization in relation to this type of system? This roundtable will facilitate a conversation about these "big" themes and questions, and why it may be necessary, important, inevitable, or a mistake, to take them on, among panelists and audience. The panel will comprise speakers who are participants in the ORA-funded Shaping AI project (2021-23) as well as interlocutors with related backgrounds.

Presenters:

Michael Castelle, University of Warwick

Christian Katzenbach, Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (HIIG)

Fenwick McKelvey, Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA)

Donato Ricci, SciencesPo médiab

Paul N Edwards, University Of Michigan

Marie-Jean Meurs, Université du Québec à Montréal

Martin Tironi

Anna Jobin, Alexander von Humboldt Institute for Internet and Society (HIIG)

Guillaume Dandurand, INRS

Session Organizer:

Noortje Marres, University of Warwick, UK

Chair:

Jonathan Roberge, Institut national de la recherche scientifique

124. Scaling the Ethical Plateaus of Energy Justice - II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Energy systems are in a state of flux. Climate change, the COVID-19 pandemic, the collapse of oil and destabilized energy economies have forced the world's energopolitical regimes (Boyer 2019) to grapple with new and evolving demands on and for energy infrastructures. These geopolitical shifts signal both emerging windows of opportunity and causes for concern, as the ethical plateaus that have come to define contemporary energy ecologies rupture at their fault lines. The growing set of diverse conceptual complements with which energy is often paired (e.g., energy rights, energy vulnerability, energy democracy, energy transitions, etc.) betray different assumptions about the scales and systems of relevance to energy politics and to processes of sociotechnical change. Energy justice, by contrast, calls for a more holistic view of the ethics informed by unique energy ecologies—i.e. the historically and culturally specific modes of relating to one's self, to other humans, to non-human life, and to the environment through one's relationship to energy and energy infrastructures. This means that more nuanced attention is needed to

account for and enact just energy relations in situ. Session #2 "Energy Policy Analysis" includes studies that critique energy policy (or the lack thereof), or offer their own takes on how energy policy can be rendered more equitable, just, or effective.

Participants:

Disrupting Justice? Utility Insecurity and the Limits of Energy Policy Morgan Sarao, Drexel University Center for Science, Technology, and Society (STS); Briana Leone, Drexel University; Andrew Rosenthal, Drexel University

Utility insecurity occurs when households are unable to pay their monthly energy bills, a situation that may result from a range of conditions including inefficient housing stock, inherited debt, lapsed communication, and other forms of socioeconomic precarity. The pandemic has both amplified disparities in utility affordability, and exposed how insecurity is normalized. Energy assistance infrastructure, designed to mitigate household vulnerability related to utility insecurity, has itself become vulnerable under pandemic conditions. How does the case of utility insecurity signal a need for energy justice as an adaptive framework? This paper draws on data from an ethnographic survey designed and administered by members of the Energy Rights Project. The survey was administered to more than 200 energy users in Philadelphia, Pennsylvania over a twelve-month period. Questions gauged utility insecurity both before and after COVID-19. In this paper we highlight "utility disruptions" -- i.e. caused by shutoffs, maintenance issues, storms, and tenant-landlord arrangements -- as well as the different forms of response that energy users leverage to what may be chronic or acute insecurity. This paper argues for holistic reform to existing energy assistance programs on local, state, and federal levels to address the expanding and nuanced needs of individuals facing energy insecurity. We argue that an analytical application of energy justice to the issue of energy insecurity in Philadelphia requires expansion of energy literacy programs, increased capacity and reach of existing energy assistance networks in Philadelphia, and public-private partnerships funding low-income residents' transition to renewable energy sources.

Energy communities as three-dimensional hybrid forums for exploring, governing and implementing energy transition. Baptiste Soubra, CNAM (National Art & Craft Conservatory) Paris; Bertrand BOCQUET, Cnam (National Art & Craft Conservatory) and University of Lille

Energy transition is made of multiple technological transformations and is complicated by the related socio-technical controversies. In France, the diversity of actors willing to take part in the energy transition increases since two decades. Community renewable energy (CRE) is developing and is allowing citizens to take part in both funding, governance and development of energy projects. Thus, through CRE citizens can take part in innovation related to energy systems. The communities operate at the boundary of the energy industry, political debates and science. Considering energy as a common, energy communities claim for bringing back energy to the citizens' control challenging the traditionally centralized state-based approach. This paper is part of PhD research which aims to contribute to the understanding of how the civil society deals with the energy transition challenges. Through grounded research and mainly semi-oriented interviews of members and partners of three french energy communities we investigate how citizens make their own question socio-technical matters related to the production of renewable energy and how they interacts with both academical, political and economical actors. We found out that through their principal activity – energy production – energy communities are involved in different ways and at different levels in research and innovation programs both locally and nationally. They contribute to the exploration of socio-political and technical possibilities regarding the implementation of the energy transition. We propose to use the dialogic space of hybrid

forums completed by an entrepreneurship dimension to analyse the development and the sustainability of energy communities.

Hydropower Development and Restorative Injustices in the Global South *Laura Castro-Diaz, Michigan State University; Maria Alejandra Garcia, Michigan State University; Maria Claudia Lopez, Michigan State University; Adam Mayer, Michigan State University*

The construction of hydroelectric dams in the Global South is promoted as a way to generate reliable and clean energy access. However, scholars, NGOs, and social movement organizations have argued that hydroelectric dams also generate a wide range of energy injustices for local and regional populations. Compensation can be seen as a way to achieve restorative justice because it aims to reduce social, economic, and environmental impacts during the construction and operation of a project. Unfortunately, compensations have been poorly implemented in dam projects. Here, we present the results of a qualitative meta-analysis of 129 papers covering 227 case studies and 87 hydroelectric projects in the Global South (from 1980-2019). We evaluated how compensation programs are restoring lost livelihoods or redressing the impacts of dams. We found that compensations are not directed to restore households and communities' lost capitals. Our results imply that dams generate negative impacts in natural, social, financial, and human capital, whereas physical capital often improves—primarily because communities are often compensated with infrastructure. Downstream and host communities often go un-compensated. We conclude by arguing that restorative injustices are rampant in hydropower development.

Just and Safe Energy Relations: Unfolding the Precautionary Principle with the Advent of Hydrogen Technologies *A. Şehnaz Kart, TUBITAK*

The COVID-19 pandemic triggered the already existing volatility in the world's energopolitical regimes to the point that the processes of sociotechnical change related to energy systems are more relevant than ever. Hydrogen is receiving unprecedented interest and investments as the post-fossil fuel world anticipates CO₂-neutral chemical conversion of energy. Total investments in the 200 hydrogen projects now existing across the value chain will exceed \$300 billion through 2030. EU is a pioneer in the promotion of a "hydrogen economy". The 2020 EU Hydrogen Strategy -flagging up to €470 billion of investment- is well aligned with the demands of the hydrogen lobby, who declared €58.6 million expenditure in 2020 trying to influence Brussels policymaking. The gas industry is in the driving seat of many new hydrogen-focused bodies/projects/lobbies, such as 'Clean Hydrogen Alliance', 'Hydrogen Europe', 'HyLAW'. On the other side of the coin, from Hindenburg to Fukushima, accidents involving hydrogen are fires and/or explosions with serious consequences for humans and the environment. In this paper I aim to make use of discourse analysis of the latest hydrogen policy papers in the EU, revealing their perception of law as a "barrier", the absence of "safety" issues therein and loopholes allowing the gas industry to continue burning fossil fuels. I approach hydrogen safety in a precautionary principle (PP) framework with ethical roots in Vorsorgeprinzip and Sic Utere; propounding its significant place in just energy relations. Lastly, I connect the normative underpinnings of PP with the governance of the advent of hydrogen technologies; asking how PP might illuminate "good relations in unequal and uncertain worlds".

Unrestored damages and lost livelihoods: Conceptualizing energy justice in Brazilian Hydropower *Adam Mayer, Michigan State University; Maria Alejandra Garcia, Michigan State University; Laura Castro-Diaz, Michigan State University; Maria Claudia Lopez, Michigan State University*

The construction of hydroelectric dams is associated with a range

of social-ecological impacts, including significant changes in the economies of rural places where large dams are often hosted. Dam builders and governments promoting hydropower have implemented compensation programs to redress the damages done by hydropower projects. In the current analysis, we apply an energy justice frame to the Jirau and Santo Antonio dams in the Madeira river basin of the Brazilian Amazon. Considering both distributional and restorative tenets of energy justice, we evaluate how these dams changed economic livelihoods and household income and whether households received compensation. Logistic regression results imply that socio-economic characteristics of households do not explain distributional inequalities in the region, but households often do not receive compensation to adequately redress damages. Further, many who report losing economic livelihoods due to the dams are not compensated. Other stated that the compensation promised by the dam authorities was not given. We argue that scholarship should advance a more expansive understanding of energy justice that situates restorative justice at its foundation, rather than the more common emphasis on procedural and distributional aspects of energy projects.

Session Organizer:

James Adams, University of California, Irvine

125. Social Studies of Science at 50: Pasts and Futures

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

The journal *Social Studies of Science* has turned 50! The journal has been one of the recognizable actors/institutions playing a role in the development, nurturing and consolidation of the field STS over those fifty years. This roundtable brings together editors and a co-founder of the journal, as well as some scholars who have recently published in it, to reflect on the past five decades, as well as the coming ones. The session will be an opportunity to bring some STS thinking to bear on one element of the path of STS.

Presenters:

roy macleod, University of Sydney

Michael Lynch, Cornell Univ.

Jess Bier, Erasmus University Rotterdam

June Jeon, Chungnam National University

Monamie Bhadra Haines

Session Organizer:

Sergio Sismondo, Queen's University

126. Art, Science, and Technology Studies - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Pre-Panel Stream: Introductions and Announcements Chair: Hannah Rogers

Participant:

Art, Science, and Technology Studies *Hannah Star Rogers, Science, Technology and Innovation Studies, The University of Edinburgh*

This commentary will be an overview of the Routledge Handbook of Art, Science, and Technology Studies (ASTS). It will highlight themes of this forthcoming book, including the role of history, touchstone art and science works, the value of STS methodologies in art, and emerging area of interest for ASTS. This paper will serve as the introduction for the related panel stream and as an editor's comment on the content, value, and potential uses of the book.

Session Organizer:

Hannah Star Rogers, Science, Technology and Innovation Studies, The University of Edinburgh

127. Borderlands and/as Machine: Technoscience in Unequal and Uncertain Lifeworlds I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Machines are central artifacts in the study of science and technology. As both the products and producers of ways of being, machines play an important role in the making and unmaking of lifeworlds. The development of converging technologies that make computing power possible is often described in frontier language. Silicon Valley and its network of engineers, technicians, and companies take on the roles of pioneers demarcating new territory for others to inhabit. This territory is positioned as a zone of encounters between various forces, a space from where human ingenuity takes flight and that is slowly populated by natives who produce new ways of thinking and of being. The language of frontiers, pioneers, and natives in technoscience brings into the fold consideration of imperial formations, that is practices, concepts, and bodies that articulate equivocal rules and areas of belonging and exclusion. This panel brings together concepts and ways of tracing relations from the fields of Feminist STS, Latina/o Studies, and Critical Ethnic Studies to think about the practices of technoscience in the making of unequal and uncertain worlds. We invite papers dealing with a range of actors and actants within and beyond the United States. Possible topics and approaches include: - Comparative racial formations and technical infrastructures - Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC) as critical actors in technoscience - Technoscience in the Borderlands - Concepts emerging from "border thinkers" as ways to bridge social and technical domains - Borderlands theory as a way to rethink STS

Participants:

Producing Value during COVID-19: Borders and Bordering Practices within Makers' PPE Supply Chains in Mexico
Veronica Uribe del Aguila, UC San Diego

Upon the collapse of the global circulation of goods in early 2020, makers worldwide deployed their shared open knowledge to create supply chains to help first responders. In Mexico, where I conducted interviews between April 2020 and February 2021, makers reoriented their practices and networks towards facial Personal Protective Equipment (PPE) production. During these months, they also produced technoscientific and sociocultural configurations that they, their brands, and other related institutions capitalized on later. This paper examines makers' practices towards value production during the first months of the covid-19 pandemic. I analyze three situations where makers use border regimes to produce value: 1) makers' labor configurations and supply chains, 2) makers' moral discourses about being a maker, and 3) the branding of DIY culture. Findings show that makers not only took advantage of deregulations procured by states and corporations to alleviate the crisis. They also repurposed Mexico's special economic zones (SEZ), generated boundaries based on moral discourses to protect a maker's commons, and enclosed DIY culture via intellectual property to maximize value production over time. Ultimately, success in these future-oriented practices, I argue, depended on makers' differential border management capacity, which reveals class and racial inequalities that discourses of openness, technological democratization, and social innovation in Mexico blur. My use of "borders" as an analytical tool resonates with political theorists Sandro Mezzadra and Brett Neilson's notion of borders as not merely geographical margins or territorial edges but complex social institutions or technologies marked by tensions between practices of border reinforcement and crossing.

Becoming/working data: colonial divisions at the digital borderlands
Jolen Martinez

This paper investigates the notion of plugging in and plugging out of digital space as a borderlands between colonial categories of the physical and informational in the context of digital colonialism in Tijuana, Mexico. I am interested in Latin American mobilities as mediated by informationalizing technologies and sciences among data-workers who build or dismantle digital worlds on both sides of the border. This paper is situated around designers, coders, and users of digital technologies and their machine ensembles. Electronic

maquiladoras surrounding Tijuana construct smart electronics and circuits while simultaneously employing smart sensors and biometric technologies to categorize and extract information from Latin American workers. Meanwhile, at the Plaza de Tecnologia, digital technologies are disassembled and reassembled, and software is uploaded and altered in a bricolage of electronic exchange. I ask how flows of information and bodies in these spaces interact in an attempt to denaturalize the sharp division between the two by attending to the neo-colonial, extractivist milieu that situate Mexican and Mexican-American digital borderlands. Further, in what ways can we learn from the borderlands and "la facultad" to address the bifurcation of information and bodies that increasingly become blurred and yet reproduced, militarized, and policed? How can we start to approach a genealogy of digital colonialism and data mining that accounts for these expansive and divided subjectivities?

Digital Games and the Racial Infrastructures of the Border
Juan Llamas-Rodriguez, University of Texas at Dallas

Racialization, as Daniel Nemser argues, takes place through spatial interventions that give rise to "groupness" and naturalize segregation. In the U.S.-Mexico border, infrastructure projects that spatialize segregation increasingly include digital spaces (camera towers, drones with mobile interfaces) in addition to physical ones. If digital networked media actively participate in the nation-state's efforts to imagine and manage the borderlands, then these media can also help us make sense of, and devise alternatives to, the visual, conceptual, and ideological infrastructures sustaining such efforts. I pursue this argument by analyzing one particular infrastructure of the U.S.-Mexico border — underground tunnels — within border-themed first-person shooter (FPS) games. Through digital modes of representation and interaction, these games create playable narratives that invoke the untamable frontier and position racialized subjects as Other, thereby encoding the racialization processes that continue to shape popular imaginings of the border. Following Tara Finkle's claim that "the infrastructure of gaming [is] itself a raced project," we must understand racialization as a ludic logic, a series of rules that limit what some subjects can do and what others cannot. Telescopic modes of visualizing the border likewise position border agents as watcher-shooters while all bodies present in the borderlands (e.g. migrants, indigenous folks) are always already targets of scrutiny and violence. My analysis of the narrative, design, and procedural elements of FPS games demonstrates how digital visualizations and their algorithmically determined forms of interaction shape the racial infrastructures of the border.

The Stories We Tell: Silicon Valley and the Use of Storytelling in Building the Smart Border Wall
Melissa Villa-Nicholas, University of Rhode Island

Borderland and ICE surveillance tech developers Anduril, Palantir, and other tech companies have built immigrant data surveillance technologies around storytelling. Storytelling, myths, and legends are not only a tool for Silicon Valley companies, but serve to position players on this particular borderlands stage- citizens, immigrants, the government, and tech companies- into a clean dichotomy of 'good versus evil' storylines. One example of these story structures are the use of Lord of the Rings references and fan culture in the Palantir and Anduril namesakes. Drawing on story taps into an innate and deeply rooted instinct within the brain and body, as well as within the social fabric that builds communities. Silicon Valley surveillance companies use storytelling to engage and justify building new borderlands through their use of science fiction, fantasy, fan culture, and video game stories. Technology companies draw on the power of story and the 'heroes journey' to bisect the 'good guys'/'antiheroes'- tech startups, designers, coders, and users, against the 'bad guys,' the undocumented immigrant, and Black and brown communities around the country that are networked into this surveillance dragnet. I argue

that the power of storytelling structures justifying and engaging tech developers in borderland surveillance technology. Through a content analysis of media, interviews, and discussion boards by Palantir employees, I look at the larger story structure of the heroes journey that shapes Silicon Valley surveillance companies and engages tech creators, employees and U.S. residents in the larger narrative of U.S.-Mexico borderland policing.

Session Organizers:

Iván Chaar López, The University of Texas at Austin
Hector Beltran

Chair:

Iván Chaar López, The University of Texas at Austin

Discussant:

Hector Beltran

128. Technology and the Attention Economy:

Postphenomenological Studies

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

In what may be a defining aspect of our contemporary world, technologies vie for our attention at seemingly all times and from seemingly all angles. The implications are both theoretical and practical. They are relevant for our theoretical understandings of the mind, the user, and the constructed notion of the subject within STS. And they have practical consequences for everything from politics, to education, to design. In this panel we take up insights from the postphenomenological perspective to explore these theoretical and practical issues. Helena De Preester starts the session by bringing in insights from the work of Bernard Stiegler to draw out the ways our attention is manipulated by neoliberal capitalism. Jesper Aagaard explores the problem of Zoom fatigue in educational contexts in relation of the COVID-19 global pandemic as schools have moved to online teaching modes. The driver distraction of smartphones and dashboard infotainment systems is investigated by Robert Rosenberger, and especially in relation to a potential future of semi-automated vehicles. And Stan Kranc brings in the work of anthropologist Edward Hutchins to consider issues of instrumental perception, explored through the case of wayfinding technologies used in navigation.

Participants:

A Stieglerian View on the Impact of Digital Technology on Attention *Helena De Preester, University College Ghent*

This contribution focuses on the topic of attention and sets forth the main points of Bernard Stiegler's analysis of the interplay between capitalist consumer society, the destruction of attention and the consequences for individual and collective life. We look at how current digital technologies in service of the needs of the market are a major factor in the destruction of attention and discuss two counterforces that do not destroy but form attention: education and meditation. If life is what you fill your attention with, then focusing or directing attention is one of the most valuable abilities for knowing how to live. Instead of letting our attention be hijacked by the market and the economic needs of neoliberal capitalism, being in charge of what happens to our attention may be a basic right that needs protection given the current conditions of the attention economy.

The Sociomateriality of Zoom Fatigue *Jesper Aagaard, Aarhus University*

Because of the COVID-19 pandemic, videoconferencing tools have become an essential part of our everyday lives as they have allowed us to keep in touch in a time of social distancing. Many people have found virtual interactions to be surprisingly exhausting, however. This has given rise to the novel concept of Zoom fatigue. The purpose of the present paper is to explore the dynamics that give rise to this peculiar phenomenon. The paper first discusses current brain-focused accounts of Zoom fatigue and argues that we should move toward a more embodied approach to social interaction. Taking departure in a postphenomenological framework, it then sets out to explore how

videoconferencing technologies mediate our social interactions, or what postphenomenologists would schematically depict as 'human-technology-human relations'. In this domain, the paper proceeds to present a preliminary list of five technologically mediated dynamics that may be thought to cause Zoom fatigue: Awkward turn-taking, inhibited spontaneity, restricted motility, lack of eye contact, and increased self-awareness. It is argued that these dynamics should make us rethink and perhaps even temper our collective expectations regarding the 'hybrid' future of remote working and learning.

Smartphone Driver Distraction and the Takeover Problem for Semi-Autonomous Cars *Robert Rosenberger, Georgia Institute of Technology*

For the last decade, including through presentations here at previous 4S conferences, I have been developing an account and public critique of the driving impairment that results from using a smartphone. A towering stack of empirical studies coming from the field of cognitive science has shown the dangers of using the phone while driving, especially texting while driving, but also handheld and hands-free phone conversation, as well as other modes such as hands-free emailing. Tools from postphenomenology and STS perspectives have proven useful for articulating these dangers in new ways. That's an important project because many drivers have proven resistant to outreach efforts, often assuming they themselves to be immune to the driving impairment of smartphone usage even as they recognize it in others. A new horizon of this problem is now emerging with the prospect of self-driving vehicles, and especially the case of semi-autonomous cars. In this case, the car will do much of the driving itself, and in some moments it will call for a human driver to "takeover." In this paper, I extend my work on the phenomenology of smartphone driving impairment to consider the problem of distracted drivers asked to suddenly takeover the driving task. If drivers cannot consistently pay attention to the road while they are in the middle of actually driving, what hope is there for relying on them to pay attention when they are at most times merely watching the car drive itself?

Wayfinding for Human-Technology Relations *Stanley C Kranc, University of South Florida*

In 2005, anthropologist Edwin Hutchins demonstrated how new cognitive entities can occasionally emerge when mental concepts are tightly combined with material "anchors", to enforce stability in reasoning processes (for instance, an abacus or wristwatch). In several respects, his analysis closely parallels Ihde's material hermeneutics in human-world relations, as explicated within postphenomenology. This paper aims to examine Hutchins' notion of cognitive blends—practical structures incorporating both mental and physical aspects—as a contribution to the understanding of instrumental perception, through a case study involving nautical navigation. Pilots routinely use range markers to guide ships visually, while avoiding hidden underwater obstructions near shore. Here, two stationary markers are remotely positioned in alignment with a known safe track. To help explain the operational technique, imagine two small lights located in a dark room, slightly separated from each other. Although deprived of other visual information, a human percipient can walk along a specific path straight towards this position by maintaining alignment with both lights. In coastal navigation, range markers constitute a remote instrument display from the pilot's perspective, such that any ship motion misaligned with the proper track produces the parallax effect. Perception accompanied by corrective action to eliminate parallax continuously revises the track of the ship. Thus, successful transit is both enabled and constrained by this instrument. Conclusions drawn from this case study suggest that current applications of visually "augmented realities" for wayfinding in unfamiliar environments may be more fully understood within the context of material anchoring, reinterpreted as a hermeneutic human-world relationship.

Session Organizer:

Robert Rosenberger, Georgia Institute of Technology

129. The politics of non-fungibility

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

This panel is concerned with fungibility as a terrain for expertise, activism, and political action. In an era when mitigation, remediation, and restoration have become routine aspects of economic development and environmental management, claims of interchangeability are both commonplace and consequential. The entities in these papers – otter habitats, port robots, aquifers, cultural landscapes, and estuaries – are embedded in relationships and ecologies that introduce problems of non-fungibility (of space, time, and kind) and raise questions about the conditions for substitution and replacement. How might we extend STS scholarship on commensuration and exchange by focusing on the limits of fungibility as a site for conceptual, political, and practical work?

Participants:

“No-otter zone”: Endangered species in spaces of conservation
Christina Dunbar-Hester, University of Southern California

Nearly exterminated in the fur trade in earlier centuries, the southern (“California”) sea otter was listed as endangered in 1977. Concerned about the vulnerability to an oil spill of the small remaining population on the central California coast, around 1990, wildlife managers attempted to relocate nearly one-tenth of these otters to an island controlled by the US Navy in the Channel Islands archipelago, over sixty miles away across open ocean. This was a failure; otters disappeared from the island. Wildlife managers were perplexed because they believed the site possessed ideal habitat (kelp forest) within otters’ historical range. They next tried releasing “ecologically naïve” young otters into the Elkhorn Slough, an estuarine area south of Santa Cruz; here otter numbers increased. Meanwhile, managers also tried to concentrate otters in a specific portion of the central coast, declaring a “no-otter zone” elsewhere along the coast; this too was a failure and the ban was lifted in 2012. Using documentary research, this paper evaluates these projects’ rationalities in their practices of conservation. The arc of otter conservation strategies revealed the willfulness of otters in terms of attachment to spaces, and a need for scientists to reevaluate their assumptions about the fungibility of space, i.e. whether habitats that seemed equivalent to humans would be received that way by otters. Though slough release strategy seemed to suit otters better, there are ongoing tensions between efforts to conserve or restore animals at the species level versus habitat/ecosystem levels, which the spatial politics of conservation help illuminate.

Labor after automation: Imagined futures on the waterfront
Mihir Anil Pandya, California State University, Long Beach

Long Beach is at the vanguard of port automation in the United States. It is the first American port complex to build a fully automated terminal. Full automation for ports means using robotic vehicles to load and unload ships and to move containers across the yard, which enables new modes of stacking, quicker turnaround times (for getting containers off ships, onto trucks and on-dock rail), all with a 50 percent reduction in emissions. The somewhat unimaginatively named Long Beach Container Terminal’s benefits come at a cost. “[Automation] is first and foremost about eliminating labor” argued a union leader at a recent Harbor Commissioners meeting. He then made the case that many others make about the second order effects of automation for vested communities. “Robots do not pay taxes, robots do not shop at our stores, robots do not buy homes ... robots do not vote.” With the Long Beach Container Terminal serving as site, this paper explores how different port workers (unionized longshoremen, casuals, truck drivers, administrative staff) deploy automation as a mediating device, a machinery that for some commensurates the seemingly incommensurable—

thriving labor markets, communities, climate, and commerce—and for many others highlights how nonfungible the future appears to be, when social, environmental, and political processes occurring at different scales and speeds, seem to drift apart rather than align.

Unfungible? Land swaps, mitigation banks, and indigenous activism in Los Angeles
Bradley Cardozo, UCLA;
Christopher Kelty, UCLA

In South Los Angeles, a “land swap” was approved recently by the California Coastal Commission. In exchange for “restoring” 30 acres of wetlands degraded by a century of oil extraction, a small oil drilling company would gain access to a different 12 acres of land — 7 acres of private property that have, thus far, been used primarily for a popular pumpkin patch and Christmas tree lot, and 5 acres of public land previously intended for ecological restoration. The restoration is financed by the oil company, who in return is allowed to increase oil production through fracking and horizontal drilling. Using a mitigation bank, other polluters in the areas—including the country’s largest port, several refineries, and other related industries—will purchase mitigation credits to offset pollution in order to fund wetlands restoration. This complex assemblage of fungibility and trading, with the laudable goal of engineering an incentive system to combat climate change, is situated on the site of the ancient villages of Puvungna and Motuচেয়গনা, sacred cultural sites of the neighboring Tongva and Acjachemen nations—sites that has been the subject of minor archaeological dispute around the “invention” of heritage as well as considerable activism by local tribal leaders and allies. Using this case as a starting point, this paper explores the complex logic of fungibility and mitigation as a challenge to indigenous activism around sovereignty and ecological restoration, and contemporary indigenous activism as a problem for governance systems built on fungibility and mitigation.

The watermaster: Tracking toxic plumes under Los Angeles
Andrew Lakoff, University of Southern California

Beneath the San Fernando Valley in northwest Los Angeles lies a vast aquifer, a potential source of local and sustainable water for the city’s population of four million. In an imagined future in which over seventy percent of the city’s water comes from local supplies, the aquifer will serve as a site of recharge and recirculation for captured rainwater and recycled wastewater. However, this vision is challenged by the specter of toxic plumes of chemicals such as trichlorethylene and hexavalent chromium that are slowly spreading across the aquifer from the dumping grounds of twentieth century industrial LA. The future of a sustainable local water supply – in which the various sources of water drawn from beneath the ground are interchangeable and allowed to flow into human bodies – hinges on the decontamination of the aquifer. To this end, the LA Department of Water and Power has embarked on a \$400 million groundwater remediation project to render the city’s groundwater fungible. This talk will focus on the work of the “watermaster,” an obscure agency whose task is to monitor contamination levels and track the spread of toxic plumes through the aquifer.

Fungibility, environmental politics, and harbor deepening in Savannah
Ashley Carse, Vanderbilt University

The Savannah Harbor Expansion Project (SHEP) is part of a decades-long effort to build a dominant logistics hub in coastal Georgia with a megaport and sprawling distribution facilities. It is, in many ways, an average project. Around the world, harbors and waterways have been deepened to accommodate ever-larger container ships. But one thing makes the SHEP stand out: half of its billion-dollar budget is dedicated to mitigating environmental impacts in the Savannah River estuary. The environmental mitigation plan called for rerouting river flows, acquiring wetlands, building a fish passage, and installing an oxygen injection system. In this sense, the SHEP may be a harbinger of

things to come. Business logistics has changed where goods are produced and how they are distributed. Among its precepts is that the routes and nodes (seaports, airports, terminals) that constitute supply chains are substitutable: cargo follows the changing path of profit maximization. Thus, place-based actors like governments, port authorities, and business associations compete to attract footloose cargo by meeting expectations of spatial fungibility. Around ports, the playbook for logistics-led economic development calls for modernizing infrastructure, improving links to landside networks, establishing conducive political conditions, and standardizing environments. But in Savannah, as elsewhere, place-based actors are legally required to protect species and other ecological entities that are embedded in relationships that complicate facile claims of substitutability. The SHEP reveals how the limits of fungibility can become a political terrain as actors negotiate the dueling imperatives to meet global logistics standards and maintain the ecological specificities of place.

Session Organizer:

Ashley Carse, Vanderbilt University

130. The Post-Truth age: What is this really about? - II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Debates on 'post truth' have become a visible staple of recent STS, the word having gathered media and journalistic attraction — though mostly in the Anglosphere — to include discussions and commentaries in some of the main journals in the field such as *Social Studies of Science and Engaging Science, Technology and Society*. However, most papers and books published on the subject of 'post truth' (within and outside STS) are presented in the form of essays or reflections that are based on little or no firsthand systematic, empirical research, and with limited geographic diversity. In this panel, we propose to bring together STS scholars interested in debating what it means to live in a post-truth age — if we are indeed living in such a new age at all — based on empirical studies. Thus, while 'post truth' is most commonly associated with the idea that contemporary societies have entered a period in which facts matter less to public opinion than emotions and personal beliefs, there remains much to be worked out in terms of what, in this respect, distinguishes the current age from others. In this panel we seek to bring together papers based on research that seeks to either rectify or destabilize a taken-for-granted, definitive and universalist definition of 'the post-truth age', based on evidence of changes to contemporary societies, in a wider variety of contexts, which would justify adopting such an all-embracing concept.

Participants:

From vaccines to masks: The manipulation of science to cause doubt *Kolina Koltai*, *University of Washington*

Science is inherently uncertain and that has been especially evident during the coronavirus pandemic. There has been a constant battle of scientists, healthcare professionals & workers, politicians, and the general public in determining what science is to be trusted. While this discourse has been elevated to the mainstream, it bears resemblance to the discussions of science pushed by anti-vaccination activists and influencers prior to the pandemic. In this paper, we examined the shift in mask sentiment and science among the anti-vaccination community. Prior to the pandemic, facial masks were generally looked upon favorably within the anti-vaccination community. Masks were seen as a better alternative to getting a flu shot to help prevent the spread of disease. During the pandemic, this narrative has drastically changed and the anti-mask movement is now often synonymous with the anti-vaccination movement. The overlap between these communities is evident. Using thematic analysis on public Instagram posts by anti-vaccine focused accounts, the paper examines this shift in sentiment. While the "science" of the masks dramatically changed, it is evident that there are consistent threads of the ways this group disagrees with the scientific mainstream and employees the use of values to push alternative scientific explanations. This paper contributes to the field of STS

by examining the ways in which science is manipulated in an alternative science community during times of global crisis.

Post-truth and Climate Change Denialism in Brazil *Jean Carlos Hochsprung Miguel*, *Federal University of São Paulo*

The article addresses some key questions about the so-called "post-truth age", denialism and its political-epistemic implications for climate change in Brazil. The text has two main objectives. The first is to present some of the main definitions of the post-truth and discuss them by the lens of "agnotology studies" (PROCTOR; SCHIEBINGER, 2008), as planned forms of production of ignorance. We suggest that the Foucauldian concept of "dispositive" helps us understand how the production of ignorance is put into practice. The second objective is to illustrate how a dispositive for producing ignorance of climate change was formed in Brazil with the rise of the "Bolsonarism", a conservative far-right movement. By the analysis of the concrete case of climate denialism in Brazil, we intend to discuss two concepts that have been explored in an excessively abstract way, the concepts of "post-truth" and "climate denialism". We argue that post-truth age is made by particular forms of circulation of discourses, materialities and meanings which serve to deny scientific facts and delegitimize certain political practices related to them. As an example, climate denialism are particular forms of circulation of discourses, materialities and meanings that aim to destroy the basis of political and epistemic sovereignty on climate change.

Post-truth during the Covid-19 pandemic: Jair Bolsonaro's denialism and personalist epistemology *Tiago Ribeiro Duarte*, *University of Brasilia*

During the Covid-19 pandemic, the Brazilian president Jair Bolsonaro became notorious for his denialism. He regularly rejected scientific advice, attacked institutions such as the World Health Organisation (WHO), and cast doubt on the data on the pandemic in Brazil. His attitudes can be understood as being part of the so-called "Post-truth age". In this paper, based on an analysis of Bolsonaro weekly lives broadcast during the pandemic, I argue that the Post-truth age is a period in which far-right populist leaders seek to transform the public debate epistemology. In Brazil, Bolsonaro attempted to do so by attacking modern institutions that have epistemic power, such as the media and the sciences, and based his denialism on a personalist epistemology through which he positions himself as the very voice of truth.

Session Organizer:

Luis Ignacio Reyes-Galindo

131. Utilizing STS Pedagogies in Design Education – II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

On June 9th, 2019, so-called "design ethicist" and former Google employee Tristan Harris, tweeted: "We need a new field of 'Society & Technology Interaction' (or STX)." The tweet caused a maelstrom of reactions from STS scholars and others, who used it as a classic example of the willful ignorance of industrial actors towards decades-old scholarship about their field. Harris eventually deleted the tweet and apologized for "a poor choice of words": "We want to see a world where the field of design...[is] equipped with an applied view of the fields you mention." This panel explores how this work is already being done and how it might continue. Arguably, Design Studies has been an STS field for over 35 years: in 1984, Hillier, Musgrove, and O'Sullivan argue that architecture should be taught alongside scientific philosophers such as Popper, Kuhn, and Lakatos; five years later, design theorist Victor Margolin uses Dickson, Feyerabend, and Aronowitz to argue that "we cannot conceive of any theory of design...independent of a theory of society" (1989); and in 2015, Cameron Tonkinwise argues that Actor-Network Theory is inherently designy. Design educators teach students to design artifacts which are necessarily embedded within sociotechnical and technoscientific systems. What, then, can STS offer the design academy? How can students connect their studio

work with its broader implications? We aim to assemble a panel of teacher-scholars who will directly address pedagogical approaches.

Participants:

Context-Centered Design: From Ethnography of Design to the Design of Ethnography and Pedagogy *Brandon Costelloe-Kuehn, 428 4th St*

This paper draws on three primary threads of research over a ten year period to argue for the relevance and timeliness of "context-centered design" in STS-rooted design education. Ethnographic research at the U.S. Environmental Protection Agency revealed how scientists were designing and developing "experimental media systems" that extended a "transmission model" of communication into an emergent practice of communication as "context production." Building on this ethnography of scientists as designers, a second thread on the Platform for Experimental Collaborative Ethnography turned the research process on itself, designing a new context for scholarly communication in STS and anthropology while developing understanding of the broader context of scholarly communication and education. A third thread, and the focus of this talk, explores how ethnography of design and the design of ethnographic projects both inform pedagogical approaches within a unique undergrad design program deployed within the context of an STS department. While there have been scattered forays into "context-centered design" (most notably in the field of human-computer interaction) this paper seeks to develop the concept as an ethnographically- and STS-informed alternative to the anthropocentrism of human-centered design. It also develops the notion of "relays" between theory and practice in a way that grounds the best of "design thinking" in the specificity and materiality that characterize particular contexts. Finally, the paper concludes with some notes on how "regenerative design" and "living systems principles" are crucial frameworks for design education in the context of climate change, mass extinction, and other converging crises.

Infiltration and prefigurative acts of resistance in the public sector *Isabella Brandalise, RMIT University*

This paper looks at two design initiatives in the public sector under the frame of prefigurative acts of resistance and "minor design activism" (Lenskjold et al, 2015). They emerge from infiltration processes – understanding rules and navigating interstices of a system in order to find opportunities for action from within it – with a pataphysical twist (Jarry, 1996; Rosenbak, 2018) – focusing on exceptions rather than the general rule. Moving away from grand narratives of government innovation, these projects are seen as small scale practices that rehearse conditions and political systems that do not conform to politics as usual, while making comments about the existing situation (DiSalvo, 2016). The first project is the narrative of an imaginary dissent-led subcommittee infiltrated in the Mayor's Office of New York City, embodied through a documentary video and pretense artifacts, which were used to prompt provocative conversations with civil servants about how things could be different (Brandalise, 2017). The second is a reflection on the value of participatory design practices of a government lab in Brazil. Beyond project deliveries, the lab has contributed to the development of new capacities in civil servants (Ferrarezi et al, 2018) by making alternative government practices visible and tangible (Tassinari, 2016). From an individual and speculative to an organizational and concrete design initiative, the aim is to reflect on the role of infiltration and prefigurative endeavors in the public sector as acts of resistance, spaces of exception that can challenge dominant structures and experience alternative ways of being. Brandalise, I. (2017). "Eventual Everyday: Infiltrating and Opening Systems through Design". In: Proceedings of Nordes 2017: Nordic Design Research Conference. Ferrarezi, E., Lemos, J., & Brandalise, I. (2018). Experimentação e novas possibilidades em governo:

aprendizados de um laboratório de inovação. Brasília, Enap. DiSalvo, C. (2016). "Design and Prefigurative Politics". In: The Journal of Design Strategies: Vol. 8, No. 1 Fall 2016. Jarry, A. (1996). Exploits and Opinions of Dr. Faustroll, Pataphysician. Boston, MA: Exact Exchange. Lenskjold, T. U., Olander, S., & Halse, J. (2015). "Minor Design Activism: Prompting Change from Within". In: Design Issues: Volume 31, Number 4 Autumn 2015. Rosenbak, S. (2018). The Science of Imagining Solutions. PhD dissertation. Umea: Umea University. Tassinari, V. (2016). "Aesthetics as Politics: a Theoretical Framework for Disruptive Design Practices". In: The Journal of Design Strategies: Vol. 8, No. 1 Fall 2016.

Sensor Autopsies – autographic perspectives on pollution *dietmar offenhuber, Northeastern University*

In my proposed presentation I reflect on the lessons from a seminar on pollution sensing and environmental justice I taught at the Princeton School of Architecture in spring 2020. The course was motivated by a discursive gap I noticed in earlier courses – students are prepared to extract environmental pollution data from EPA data bases and use these datasets to examine environmental justice issues, but often take the data at face value, overlooking the infrastructural arrangements of data collection as well as the material aspects of sensing, which often play a crucial role in environmental debates between grassroots initiatives and public authorities. The seminar aimed to develop a framework for the production, use, and critique of environmental data from a material perspective—by examining and critiquing public data infrastructures, learning how grassroots initiatives collect material evidence to challenge official accounts, and finally, developing analog sensing mechanisms for environmental phenomena. The students conducted "sensor autopsies," dismantling sensors to study their material underpinnings and how they interact with environmental phenomena. In a final exercise, students designed experiments that visualize pollution through material proxies available in their immediate, COVID locked-down environments. For design students, it was an unusual experience to approach STS theory through the process of making, and recognize data as inherently material artifacts shaped through human practices. Pollution was no longer a number above a threshold value, but an autographic phenomenon materially inscribed into bodies and land.

Theory as material practice: Playing with formats for reconfiguring ethnography in design education with STS pedagogies *Hannah Maria Varga, Humboldt University Berlin*

As a STS anthropologist and studio course teacher, I would like in this talk to reflect on how STS perspectives and sensibilities can provide alternative approaches to concepts such as the 'user', 'customer' or 'utility' by integrating ethnographic research into the studio courses. Drawing inspiration from my PhD research at a school of architecture in Spain and my own teaching experience at a design faculty in Austria I would like to present two teaching formats: (1) the ethnographic visual reading group and (2) the 'cosmogram' as a material architecture of field notes, which have been developed and explored as part of studio courses in these two countries. Both these formats have been developed as critical perspectives through making on the social as 'socio-technical assemblages'. With these examples of STS anthropology inspired formats for design students I would like to open the discussion on: how contemporary developments in ethnography can enhance design education as well as how design can enhance ethnographic methods and theories in return? And, further: how could we think of theories as material design practices to enrich design processes beyond the education?

Session Organizers:

Gabriel Schaffzin, York University, Toronto
Zachary Kaiser, Michigan State University

132. The University and Academic Knowledge Production:

Challenges to Expertise

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

This panel will explore the future of the university in terms of the relations the university has with its academic knowledge producers. Over the course of the 20th century, the university was the premier site of knowledge production, distribution, and certification, and was viewed as the gold standard for epistemic authority. Developments in the first two decades of the 21st century have challenged this status. The Internet, which lacks any epistemic gate-keeping, is the main source of knowledge for most people, and most research today is conducted by private entities, outside the university setting. Neoliberal reforms of the university have rendered it captive to clients needs and goals. This dependence has contributed to the crisis of epistemic authority that is sometimes referred to as the "post-truth society". Since university faculty are experts in their fields, the crisis of epistemic authority is also a crisis of expertise, especially with regard to sensitive and hotly contested issue, where experts disagree or are sometimes proven just wrong: Brexit, the 2016 US election, the Covid-19 pandemic. To address the issue of practices and methods in unequal and uncertain worlds for the university, the first three papers are on the changing nature of knowledge and university and the related last two papers are on academic expertise. These papers are on: STS's response to changes to the university in post-Covid times; the impact of emergent technologies such as artificial intelligence on the changing nature of humanity and on higher education; the difference of the neoliberal notion of scientific knowledge as a public good and the Pasteur's Quadrant notion of scientific knowledge as a public good in which universities and scientists from non-academic settings cooperate on use-inspired basic scientific research, what we can learn from doubt in the seventeenth century on academic expertise and STS's problem with anti-expertise due to knowledge from minority and indigenous groups.

Participants:

The Last of the Handcraft Industries: STS and the Post-Covid University *Robert Frodeman, Independent researcher*

In an age of ubiquitous technology the university has remained one of the last hand-craft industries. Thousands of professors teach nearly identical courses across thousands of institutions across the US and other countries, and publish research that often goes uncited. The 20th century research university has been ripe for disruption; covid has provided the catalyst. Likely changes include the continued shift to online education, the closure of a number of colleges and universities, the growth of university-corporation partnerships, and the breakdown of the inward-focused disciplinary research culture of many disciplines. This talk explores how STS can respond to these changes, and will describe the development of a type of practice that I and others call field philosophy.

Emerging Technologies and the Automation of Higher Education *Alcibiades Malapi-Nelson, Humber College*

Emergent Technologies (i.e., cognitive science, artificial intelligence, virtual reality, biotechnology and biomechanics) are opening up new avenues of empirical and theoretical exploration that are fundamentally questioning what it means to be human – triggering profound social, moral and legal repercussions. I will attempt to articulate the possible consequences of this upcoming 'humanity 2.0' for higher education and its outcomes. Departing from the premise that teaching-oriented academia is priming itself for its machine-replacement, I shall focus on the foreseeable effect of artificial intelligence both on higher education itself and on the sustainability of employment that shall arrive from the seemingly inevitable widespread adoption of this technology. A modified method of knowledge-delivery, better prepared for the challenge of pervasive automation, will be suggested. Unlike the popular – largely negative – narrative concerning the general effect of technology upon education and work, my position does not associate doom with these disruptive innovations. Instead, it embraces them by recasting the question regarding 'the human' from an ontological fixation to a

normative value, while shifting the ethical framework from a traditional, precautionary stance to a bolder, proactionary one.

Scientific Knowledge as a Public Good and The University *Francis Remedios, Independent Scholar*

With the challenges to the university on many issues including uncertainty, epistemic authority and social justice, a key issue is the changing notion of scientific knowledge as a public good. This paper compares the neoliberal version of scientific knowledge as a public good in which the public should have academic training to improve the knowledge economy to versions of scientific knowledge as a public good, which include academic scientists from universities and from outside of universities to solve . The neoliberal version of scientific knowledge as a public good is represented by the approach in *Designing the New American University* (Crow and Dabars 2015) in which the research university should address the higher educational needs of society. Arizona State University's (ASU) President Michael Crow changed ASU to be ranked as the top innovative university in the US and to an adaptive knowledge enterprise. In *The Fifth Wave* (2020), Crow and Dabars discuss how to bring university to more students of diverse backgrounds and to align teaching to accommodate these students together with academic excellence and broad accessibility. In contrast, Donald Stokes' Pasteur's Quadrant's version of scientific knowledge as a public good is based on use-inspired notion of basic scientific research which involves private foundations such as the Rockefeller Foundation and corporate R&D units and universities. Another version of science as a public good similar to Stokes' version is Defence Advanced Research Projects Agency (DARPA), which is a US government funded organization within an ecosystem brings together universities, corporate, government and the public together to solve unforeseen scientific knowledge problems for national security. This paper will discuss which version will better address the problems of the science as a public good and the university, which face uncertainty and problems of epistemic authority.

Doubt as Epistemic Generator *Sharon Rider, Uppsala University*

"Modernity" can be seen as a name for how we have handled post-truth conditions for 500 years. The middle of the early modern period was a time of extreme social and economic instability and political upheaval, on the one hand, and exceptional scientific, cultural and artistic fecundity, on the other. Religious wars engulfed Europe, crop failure, famines and epidemics caused turmoil, the many trials and executions mark it as the peak of witch-hunt hysteria. But the Renaissance had enlarged the historical, geographical and scientific image of man and the world, and gave rise to the Age of Discovery and the Scientific Revolution. The *Zeitgeist* was to question and doubt: the authority of religion (the Bible) as well as of science (Aristotle), the legitimacy of the Church as well as the Crown. Received truths and traditional rules of judgment were destabilized; if nothing was certain, anything was possible. The grounds and prospects of reason were then as now a hot topic. Descartes, despite the handy skills he attained from his years of study at La Flèche, felt cheated. Seeking secure grounds for knowledge, such that he might judge and direct himself in life without guidance from others, he found neither certitude nor wisdom. The new way of thinking that he later introduced caused strife within universities, but proved too epistemically productive to be suppressed. Perhaps we exaggerate the uniqueness of our present state; we can learn something about the rise and fall of academic expertise from a consideration of seventeenth-century struggles over knowledge.

STS' Epistemic Heart of Darkness: Expertise, Counter-Expertise or Simply Anti-expertise? *Steve Fuller, University of Warwick*

From its inception, STS has been haunted by a reflexive problem:

What sort of science is ‘science of science’ – assuming that it is a sort of science at all? For some, notably Harry Collins, the answer is fairly straightforward, namely, that STS offers expertise about expertise, understood as a project that sits comfortably alongside the experts that it studies. Indeed, these experts might become more reflective practitioners as a result of STS. However, Collins’ vision appears to be in the minority. Much more common has been the idea of STS as offering counter-expertise by providing an epistemic articulation to groups that would otherwise have voice or presence in matters that affect them. This second vision has undergone a significant metamorphosis over the last half-century. Originally these groups were understood as lay people or scientists and technologists in subordinate positions – what Steven Shapin memorably called the ‘missing masses’. However, in recent years, greater attention has been given to ‘alternative’ forms of knowledge associated with minority or indigenous peoples. The third vision, anti-expertise, problematizes the very idea of expert identities. This radically constructivist position proceeds from two premises: (1) that individuals are members of multiple groups at once and hence have multiple identities; (2) that groups do not possess well-defined bodies of knowledge that are their exclusive property. The post-truth condition dwells in this third possibility. And while STS has much to contribute to it, the field’s practitioners remain reluctant to embrace it. My talk will focus on this problem, which currently inhibits STS’s own voice in public discourse.

Session Organizer:

Francis Remedios, Independent Scholar

133. Using Speculative Fictions for Pedagogical/Research Applications Centered Around Environmental Stewardship, Responsibility, and Responsible Innovation

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:

Developing Grounded Speculations: Method, Case Studies, and Questions *Danial Qaurooni, 325 E. 10th St.*

Kim Fortun (2012) has called our contemporary condition Late Industrialism, in recognition of all the ways in which functionalism in design has failed us. Functionalism promised us that form would follow function, designs would not leak, and side effects would be insignificant. As Fortun reminds us, however, “the levee has broken... retention walls have failed,” and e-trash, radioactive waste, and plastic pollution are both piling up and being suppressed out of sight and mind. As she grapples with the failures of this functionalist logic all around us, Fortun pleads with anthropologists to reorient themselves and retool their ethnographic methods for the conditions of Late Industrialism. In this presentation, we argue that Fortun’s plea can and should be translated to design in general, and speculative methods in particular. This practice of speculating out of a contemporary time and place is what we have elsewhere called Grounded Speculations. In a recently published pictorial (Smith & Qaurooni, 2020), we experimented with this method by grounding a series of speculative designs out of the Chernobyl Exclusion Zone, a fenced and protected area that was established after the notorious nuclear meltdown of 1986 in order to limit radioactive contamination by cordoning off the most toxic area. Here, we use examples from this work as well as unpublished materials to highlight some of the salient methodological commitments of Grounded Speculations, including its relationship to futuring, functionalism, world-building, and the public.

Escaping the Bog: Enacted Speculative Fictions for Wetland Conservation *Cameron Butler, York University*

Through its 30-year history, the Burns Bog Conservation Society has improved public awareness and care for Burns Bog in Delta,

British Columbia, one of the largest urban peat bogs in North America. Beginning in 2016, the BBCS began hosting a series of “Bog Escape” events—escape room-styled narrative scavenger hunts—held within the small publicly-accessible portion of the bog. Within these events, participants act out either 1) (supernatural) historical narratives of early British settlers discovering the bog or the haunting of the bog by the ghosts of soldiers who were killed in WWI by American bombs produced with peat extracted from the bog; 2) fantastical tales of forest pixies and wizards; or 3) dystopian futures of an unbreathable world following the destruction of the bog. I theorize these Bog Escape events as forms of enacted speculative fiction that invite participants to become invested in the conservation of the bog by embodying these narratives. By inviting the public to enter and then ‘escape’ the bog, the BBCS asks participants to physically (re)create a people-less nature, one that is always in danger of ‘human impact’ (i.e., presence). In particular, I argue that the over-arching narratives of discovery, destruction, mystery, and threat employ speculative fiction to legitimize settler-colonial property regimes and land conservation, foreclosing the possibilities of Indigenous modes of land stewardship or care. The Bog Escape reveals the tensions and limitations of conservation fictions that imagine humans as purely destructive environmental forces.

Exploring Planetary Design Futures Through Kim Stanley Robinson’s Speculative Fictions *May Ee Wong*

This paper reflects upon engagements with Kim Stanley Robinson’s speculative fictions space-ark epic *Aurora* (2015) and climate-crisis fiction *Ministry of the Future* (2020) as research/pedagogical tools in exploring the possibilities and challenges of planetary design. Offering a brief conceptualisation of Kim Stanley Robinson’s speculative fiction as examples of ‘worlding’ which follow feminist STS philosopher Donna Haraway’s notion of worlding in which ‘it matters what worlds world worlds’ (2016), I discuss this in relation to two contexts in which these speculative fictions are explored: 1) the reading of *Aurora* by the Feminist Speculative Fiction Book Club based in UC Davis that brings together graduate students and researchers from various disciplines interested in the intersections of speculative fictions and feminist visions of ecological futures, and 2) *Ministry of the Future* as a text assigned for the interdisciplinary seminar *Histories of World-Making in Science, Design and Technology* that I am teaching at Nanyang Technological University. I argue that Kim Stanley Robinson’s novels present scenarios that critique techno-utopianism and ideologies of environmental governance and design through the narratives’ focus on problem-solving. The pragmatic scope of these speculative fictions offer dramatic worlds that are entangled with the implications of our contemporary global environmental conditions. These prompt readers to reflect upon the consequences of the employment of technology taken to logical ends and also the scope of human responsibility and agency. I suggest these grim speculative fictions as planetary design futures could generate insights into articulating a more ethical and eudaimonistic vision of planetary environmental stewardship.

Futures writing as creative un/worlding *Horst Rachel, The University of British Columbia*

In this paper I explore how narrative inquiry into future potentiality can be a performative methodology for cultivating curiosity in and empathy for the future other. In my capacity as a graduate student in Language and Literacy Education, and my work in the Digital Literacy Centre at the University of British Columbia, I have been developing and presenting futures making and writing workshops for teacher candidates and graduate students. These workshops are designed to catalyze creative and embodied futures thinking and imagining about the technologies and artifacts we build and become with, and the futures that emerge from our entangled relationships with material world(s)

and contingency. New materialism provides a theoretical framework for writing as inquiry into future imaginaries that are inclusive of the extraterrestrial and interplanetary. In this paper, I share insights both on the futuring methodology as well as from the creative output elicited in these writing and making workshops, much of which veers into outer space where the writer/inquirer is able to experiment in realities beyond the confines of the human-centric and Earth-bound present. Growing out of a post humanist ontology that troubles boundaries between now and then, Earth and space, the human and the other-than-human, this work promotes creative engagement in the thick assemblage of intra-acting agencies in imagined times, bodies, and places.

Session Organizers:

Shannon N. Conley, James Madison University
Brenda Trinidad

134. Coastalization: Thinking global relations from the coast - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

CASTING THE GROUND: Singapore's Land Reclamation Projects and the Construction of Territory. *Hans Hans, ETH Zurich*

Singapore's state-led strategy of making land from the sea has been comparable to a form of alchemy in which governmental agencies create prime sites and high returns "out of nothing." The island-state's rapid urbanisation together with its pursuit for territorial expansion through land reclamation propelled it to the number one spot in the planetary ranking of natural sand imports. Approximately one-quarter of the island-state's land area has been artificially added. Sand has not only shaped the island-state's physical form but nearly segment of its urban development. Used as material component of concrete, the sand supplied by a transnational trading industry has fueled the country's public housing program, in which over eighty percent of Singaporean residents live. Newly reclaimed land has also enabled the expansion of infrastructures and industries serving Singapore's global economic ambitions — more than 40% of the island-state's GDP is earned on reclaimed land. In effect, a series of inaccessible parcels have cordoned off the city from the sea and less than ten percent of the coastline is publicly accessible. The steady flow of sand across national borders has been central to the development of a repertoire of characteristic political and regulatory strategies that shaped Singapore's urban and national identity. By examining how sand is turned into soil, I reflect on the urbanism of sand accumulation as a project of urban and territorial design. Tracing the process of land reclamation — from territories of extraction to the sites of accumulation — the research highlights the metabolic relations between the city and its hinterland. I will describe why the unprecedented scale of land reclamation is important to Singapore, how sand trade is justified and how soil is recast as an urban project.

Concrete Modernities and Navigational Practices: Processes of Coastalization at a Sierra Leone Wharf *Cecilie Baam, Aarhus University*

Life in coastal communities is built around the movements of water and a cyclical timescape. In the coastal town of Tombo, Sierra Leone, the skills and knowledges that people develop, employ and make use of are in constant change. My paper is ethnographically oriented, largely focused on socioeconomic and material relations on the shoreline and at sea, as well as the different skills people make use of to get 'their daily fish'. Drawing on Henrik Vigh's notion of social navigation, understood as "the interactivity of practice and the intermorphology of motion [highlighting...] how people move and manage within situations of social flux and change" (Vigh, 2009: 420), I describe what I call a fluid economy of skills in

Tombo. This is a dynamic and ever-innovative form of skilled adaptation to the environment, infrastructure and activities, where different skills and knowledges, are learned and mastered through working in a fluid social and material landscape, or rather, seascape. This navigational approach to life on the coastal frontier, is contrasted with a developmental vision of a concrete land—water border, materialized in this paper by two development projects centering on wharf infrastructure. I label these visions of concrete modernity, emphasizing the incongruencies between these and the fluid socioeconomic practices people make use of to make their ends meet. Finally, I introduce the community facilitator as a Bourdieuan bricoleur, to argue how for the people in the communities, development projects fold into the continual fluid cycles of temporalities, tides and opportunities, that appear, and reappear, but never as the same as before.

Congested Coasts and Hospitable Hinterlands: Dry Ports in Germany and Kazakhstan *Verena La Mela, University of Fribourg*

The Covid-19 pandemic showed the vital importance of dry ports as alternative infrastructures to sea ports. During the pandemic flights suspended and borders closed while at the same time the demand of goods increased. The flood of cargo led to a congestion of coastal ports and thus inland transportation routes along the "New Silk Road" became an attractive alternative. Dry ports are linked to sea ports through rivers or canals, railways and roads. Similar to coastal infrastructures they are meeting places of people, goods, technologies and forms of governmentality, which interact there in new and often unexpected ways. In this paper I focus on two nodes on the "New Silk Road", Khorgos dry port on the Sino-Kazakh border and Nuremberg intermodal container terminal to test the applicability of the concept of "marginal hubs" (Marsden and Reeves 2019). Applying this concept, I analyse them as centres of social and economic gravity which produce a multiplicity of human and non-human relationships. Marginal hubs — as Marsden and Reeves see it — are localities, neither urban nor rural, geographically peripheral and far from political centres. In spite of their claimed marginality, they are sites of intensive interaction and bring about new forms of sociability. By looking at these two seemingly very different logistical hubs in Europe and Central Asia I identify their commonalities which escape casual observation. The paper is based on a long-term anthropological research conducted at the Sino-Kazakh border, as well as in Germany, both before and during the Covid-19 pandemic.

Flotsam and Jetsam: Encounters with Debris on Canada's West Coast Trail *Lauren Harding, University of Saskatchewan*

The West Coast Trail is a multi-day wilderness trek that follows a section of southwestern Vancouver Island called Canada's shipwreck coast. Managed by the state as a national park, this designated wilderness area crosses the traditional territory of the Pacheedaht, Ditidaht, and Huu-ay-aht First Nations. In this paper, I draw on anthropological scholarship on ruins, debris, and rubble to investigate encounters of hikers with "unnatural" objects washed up onshore. I suggest that hikers, as tourists, are positioned to ignore how the objects of their beachcombing fascination are connected to environmentally destructive processes. Furthermore, I show how the state planning of infrastructure and the changing routes of global trade have constructed this place as wilderness, despite its imbrication with the processes of imperialism, colonialism, and capitalism. Clear signs that the space traversed by the West Coast Trail is part of larger networks of mobility and change are littered across its length in complex tangles of flotsam and jetsam. Hikers encounter the rusted bones of cargo ships jutting through the sand, floats and buoys from fishing operations litter the trail, and, more ominously, plastic detritus from the 2011 tsunami in Japan wash up onshore. I discuss how the various flotsam and jetsam

along the trail expose the dynamic non-human and human forces that render it a paradoxical space of remoteness and connection, of resource extraction and tourist veneration, and of Indigenous resilience and settler nation-building.

From the Front Lines of Supply to the Margins of the State: Reimagining Infrastructure of the Northern Sea Route (NSR) *OLGA POVOROZNYUK, UNIVERSITY OF VIENNA; Peter Schweitzer, Department for Social and Cultural Anthropology, University of Vienna*

The town of Tiksi in northeastern Siberia was founded in the heydays of Soviet exploration of the Arctic and is proudly called “the arctic sea-gate of Yakutiya” for its geographical location as a maritime and riverine transportation node. The community development reached its peak by the 1980s along with the maximum bulk of goods supplied from around the world by sea. As the state withdrew its support and investments in coastal infrastructures, the once bustling sea port of Tiksi turned into a peripheral navigation point and an assemblage of decaying port facilities and ship-breaking yards. Today, the sea port only manages to survive due to sporadic logistic service and cooperation with an NSR search and rescue base located in Tiksi. The current modernization program of the NSR, widely propagated in official discourses and in the media, promises a new infrastructural and socioeconomic boom. In this program and in the imagination of community residents, the sea port again becomes a central node for large-scale state-supported development. Yet, the majority of the modernization plans remain on paper and maps: the non-existent passenger terminal prevents international cruise ship tourism, the long-delayed dredging of the port complicates navigation, and the replacement of the old harbor cranes is only hoped for. This paper, based on an ethnographic study of the coastal community of Tiksi, argues for understanding infrastructures as promises and political projects through which the state can articulate and reassert its presence on the margins of its power reach.

Session Organizer:

Arne Harms, Institute of Anthropology - University of Leipzig

135. Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy/Session 1: Fractured Consensus

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

The Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy (CompCoRe) project, comprising over sixty scholars with interdisciplinary expertise in STS, law, public policy, and the social sciences, has spent a year analyzing national policy responses to the pandemic in sixteen countries across five continents (website: compcore.cornell.edu). Our analysis shows that the pandemic is not simply a public health crisis to be managed by listening to “science” as conventional wisdom would have it. Rather, the Covid-19 crisis is playing out in unexpected and non-linear ways within the interlocking arenas of public health, economy, and politics against a continually shifting terrain of scientific, socioeconomic, and political developments. Our research identifies patterned responses across countries that demonstrate how the pandemic found and exacerbated underlying structural weaknesses in national response systems, and it highlights the need for reforms in current institutional approaches to preparedness in global health crises. Countries represented in CompCoRe include Australia, Austria, Brazil, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, Peru, Singapore, South Korea, Sweden, Taiwan, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The panel will feature comparative analyses of national efforts to enroll reliable epidemiological and biomedical expertise, resolve difficult trade-offs, manage the economic fallout of the pandemic, and build political support for effective implementation, among other topics. We aim to open up new questions about public health sovereignty, crisis management, and global flows of knowledge and power among experts, states, and citizens. You can learn more about CompCoRe at compcore.cornell.edu.

Participants:

Opening Remarks: Covid Comparisons and Lessons from the Pandemic *Sheila Jasanoff, Harvard University*

Covid-19 in Germany: Imaginaries of Stability, Institutionalized Public Reason, and the Boundaries of Solidarity. *silke beck, UFZ Leipzig; Sebastian Michael Pfotenhauer, Technical University Munich*

During the “first wave” of Covid-19, Germany was widely featured by analysts and governments around the globe as a success story of a rational, well-managed crisis response. Compared to other countries, Germany displayed a consistent and trustful delegation of matters to scientific authority and public institutions, swift and forceful economic relief measures, and little public controversy. Yet, following a country-wide reopening during the summer, Germany was taken by surprise by a severe second wave that endures well into 2021, and that has revealed fissures in previous certainties and the (self-)image as an effective crisis manager. In this paper, we trace the evolution of the German Covid-19 response since December 2019.

Drawing on research from the comparative CompCoRe study, we focus on the three interrelated domains of public health (e.g. the epistemic authority granted to certain groups and scientific constructs), economics (e.g. implied understandings of justice and the public good in the bailout efforts), and politics (e.g. the desire for consensus between federal and state levels). We show how Germany’s response reflects, on the one hand, a political culture committed to rational and consensual responses based on highly institutionalized forms of public reasoning. On the other hand, it reflects a deep aversion to risk and possible disruptions of social and economic stability, both shaped by historical experiences. We discuss how Germany’s Covid response has brought on unexpected debates about institutional reflexivity and reflects an evolving understanding of solidarity that differs markedly, for example, from the post-2008 financial crisis.

Behind South Korea’s COVID-19 Success Narrative:

Contestations over Openness, Transparency, and Democracy *Sang-Hyun Kim, Sogang University; Buhm Soon Park, Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology (KAIST)*

South Korea’s achievement in flattening the COVID-19 infection curve—without imposing compulsory lockdowns and other severely restrictive measures—has been praised internationally. Encouraged by global recognition, the Korean government has actively publicized the seeming success in containing COVID-19 with an official narrative of “K-bangyeok” (which means a uniquely Korean-style infectious disease prevention and control). The government has also claimed that this success can be attributed to its firm commitment to the three core principles of openness, transparency, and democracy implying that the COVID-19 case demonstrates a clear break with the previous conservative governments. Indeed, the ruling party’s landslide victory in the 2020 general election owed much to such perception. However, a close examination shows a far more complicated picture than the official narrative suggests. From the beginning of the pandemic, South Korea’s response to COVID-19 have generated conflicts and instabilities—especially around issues such as public versus for-profit healthcare services, socioeconomic inequality and injustice, privacy and civil rights, and the proper role of experts in democratic governance. The government’s claim of success against the pandemic has continued to be contested - occasionally by conservative political forces, but more frequently by progressive public health and other social movement activists. The latter, in particular, has challenged the very idea of K-bangyeok, the government’s conceptions of openness, transparency, and democracy, as well as the underlying prevailing sociotechnical imaginary that nourishes technocracy, developmentalism, and nationalism. By focusing on selected disputes over South Korea’s infectious disease prevention and control policies, this presentation will

argue that the country's supposedly successful containment of COVID-19 is not as self-evident as it may first appear.

Contentious Management: Singapore's Mechanisms for Pandemic Control and Enclosure *Sharad Pandian, Nanyang Technological University; Ian McGonigle, Nanyang Technological University*

With the total number of residents who died from COVID-19 in the low double digits as of the beginning of 2021, Singapore's response to the pandemic has indubitably been a relative success. While compliance by residents was crucial, it is important to not dismiss Singaporeans as simply inherently compliant. Rather, this presentation will explore the role of mechanisms for disciplining residents and the information available to them in avoiding protracted controversies regarding and disruptions to the socio-political order desired by its leaders. We explore episodes of contention that arose, including over the series of infection clusters in the low-wage migrant worker dormitories, as well as the doubts about the contact tracing app TraceTogether, showing how critics were able to muster considerable resistance online briefly. However, Singapore's singular political and media infrastructure ensured that these contentions were managed quickly enough for the government to retain legitimacy, instead of haemorrhaging it, as might have happened through a sustained interrogation by a critical, or even independent, media ecosystem. Ultimately, the case of Singapore serves as a challenge to the assumption that liberal democratic decision-making remains the sole epistemically viable option for "successful" political organization.

Session Organizers:

Sheila Jasanoff, Harvard University

Stephen Hilgartner, Department of Science & Technology Studies/ Cornell University

Ben Hurlbut, Arizona State University

Onur Ozgode, Harvard STS Program, Harvard Kennedy School

Margarita Rayzberg, Cornell University STS

136. Digital (Un)wellness: Power, Health, and Screen Time - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Contested Screens: The Social Construction of Remote Educational Technology in the COVID-19 Pandemic *Katie Day Good, Miami University*

The shift towards distance learning during the COVID-19 pandemic has led to new uses and characterizations of technology in education. One year into the pandemic, two-thirds of K-12 students in the United States were learning remotely, either full-time or part-time (Ipsos, 2021). The pandemic hastened the digitalization of learning, and a transition to 1:1 computing models, that had been underway in public education for over a decade (Zierer, 2019). These changes contributed to a surge in daily internet use and "screen time" among children, touching off contentious debates about the roles of digital technology in their education and wellbeing. With teachers, parents, students, health professionals, and technology producers all thrust into new roles as users, evaluators, or promoters of educational technology in a pandemic, they became identifiable "relevant social groups" that contributed to the social construction of technology (SCOT) (Bijker et al., 2012). This paper uses a SCOT approach to map the predominant social groups and discourses that gave meaning to remote learning technology in the pandemic. Analyzing mainstream press coverage of school reopening debates during the 2020-2021 school year, it argues that these groups cast remote learning technology, such as Zoom, as a charged symbol of the closure of school buildings and attendant in-person activities and services. Groups variously heralded and disputed digital technology's

value as a tool for protecting children from harm and promoting community health. Their discourses foreground, for scholars, the importance of attending to questions of care, especially for children, in understanding the social meanings of technology.

Maintaining posture, changing habits. Screen work and responsible ergonomics *Joeri Bruyninckx, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Maastricht Univer*

Increased mobile device and screen time have been associated not just with new habits of attention, but also with habits of bad body posture, such as hunching, slouching or slumping. (Often moralized) concerns over keeping good posture are age-old. Yet recently, some medical professionals have associated media use with an "epidemic" of musculoskeletal syndromes, such as 'text neck'. Such concern has been accompanied by a plethora of wearables, clothing, cushions and desktop-sensors that aim to monitor, correct and strengthen 'good posture'. STS studies of bodily practice have repeatedly underscored the difficulty of standardizing and configuring bodies. Such work as well as critical studies of self-tracking have highlighted various processes of surveillance, disciplining and distributed of corporeality at play. Yet the process by which bodies form durable habits remains under-theorized. Taking these posture analytics applications as a starting point, I examine technologies for making, re-fitting and maintaining posture within a changing socio-material environment. I draw on a qualitative document analysis of promotional materials, patents and documentation of the design and models underlying three contemporary 'smart' posture adjusting devices. Reading these against the background of discourses around 'digital health' among office workers since the 1970s, I show how the modelling of "healthy" postures and the responsibility for enacting these have shifted over time, thus calling attention to the elaborate apparatus of design, research, legislation and use. Tracing the re-making of modern posture, I argue, offers new insights into the various ways in which bodies become habituated by pressing against technology.

The Cultural Work of Affective Computing in the Age of Zoom Fatigue *Brendan Smith, University of Toronto*

Since the beginning of the COVID-19 pandemic, Zoom fatigue has emerged as a prominent term in technopathological discourse, which refers to mental and bodily experiences of distress incurred through working remotely while regularly using videoconferencing software. At the same time, companies such as Affectiva, one of the world's largest technology firms developing 'emotional AI', are positioned uniquely as experts who can produce technical solutions to emergent technopathologies such as Zoom fatigue. The purpose of this paper is to trace the discursive power of affective computing technologies through an examination of its links with technical means of viewing psychopathology developed since the 19th century. This also follows the purpose of media genealogy which is to provide a 'history of the present'. This paper takes up media genealogy's problematization approach as its methodology. This is an approach which adopts Foucault's term of problematization to understand how something has come to be thought of in terms of a problem to be solved by technical means; something which has become entangled within contested claims of truth and falsity, and the production of technologically-mediated subjectivities. Through this paper, I will argue that affective computing solutions to technopathologies such as Zoom fatigue produce cultural imaginaries that follow a historically contingent, neurological logic of digital reductibility: a logic that makes everything problematic about the human reducible into digital bits and bytes that can only be made useful through cybernetic neuro-synthesis between human and machine.

The Uses of Distraction: Doomscrolling, Losing Time, and Digital Well-being in Pandemic Space-times *Jacob Saindon, University of Kentucky*

In the space-times of the COVID-19 global health crisis, how

have our relationships with smartphones changed? How do popular discourses designate mundane engagements with digital technologies as healthy or unhealthy, and how are these notions of wellness practiced? This paper draws upon an online survey of smartphone users residing in Kentucky, and a review of marketing, journalistic, and academic literature to establish current understandings of 'digital well-being'. The paper then analyzes interviews with Kentucky smartphone users residing in Louisville, Lexington, and Bowling Green who were asked to track their screen time for a one-week period. This project reveals normative conceptions of well-being and the role of smartphone and screen time metrics in producing ideas of digital wellness. The paper draws upon health geographies, disability studies, media studies, and STS to argue that the common heuristics of digital wellness are insufficient to either understand or improve subjective well-being, and that a relational and ecological analysis of 'digital well-being' allows us to re-evaluate normative prescriptions of care. Mobilizing theories of attention and neoliberal biopolitics in particular, the paper connects normative notions of attentiveness and wellness to demonstrate a specific assemblage of 'digital well-being.'

Session Organizers:

Chad Valasek, University of California at San Diego

Laura Calloway, Indiana University

Alex Beattie, Victoria University Wellington

Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley

137. Relating with STS from South Asia I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

At the 2020 4S/EASTS conference, the panel "Locating South Asia in Social Studies of Science and Technology" aimed to bring together research on South Asia that are otherwise scattered across different topical 4S panels. By bringing together the research communities of South Asia, it aimed to render visible and consolidate conceptual vocabularies, epistemological, ontological and ethical concerns, and methods involved in researching South Asia. This year's panel is a "bridgework" that draws together the ongoing effort to revisit different pasts of STS in South Asia to intervene in its present and explore possible future avenues for research, collaboration, interdisciplinary and transnational speculations. Papers that explore the following questions are welcome to apply: 1) How does the STS work in South Asia relate with STS areas and theories including Sociology of Scientific Knowledge, Actor-Network Theory, New Materialisms, Indigenous and Postcolonial Studies? 2) How do such theories when applied to the context of South Asia emerge with unique sensibilities in your research? 3) How can relating STS to anthropological and sociological work on scientific knowledge and technoscientific development in South Asia question "the imperialism of [Global North] categories" in research as an effort towards decolonializing STS (Lal)? 4) What are the other sciences that are possible in "a world of sciences" and technologies when technoscience is viewed "from below?" (Harding; Wiley) Hence, this panel also aims to investigate the diversity loss in sciences and livelihood losses due to the (de-)legitimizing tactics of modern science. Papers that focus on any STS areas in the context of South Asia including but not limited to technoscientific development of nation states, computational politics, legal, social and environmental justice, public understanding of science, Anthropocene, and postcolonialism may apply. Bibliography Harding, Sandra G. 2008. *Sciences from below: Feminisms, Postcolonialities, and Modernities*. Durham: Duke University Press. Lal, Vinay. 2010. "Thesis Two: Postcolonialism Has Had Nothing to Say about the Imperialism of Categories." Lal Salaam: A Blog by Vinay Lal Reflections on the Culture of Politics & the Politics of Culture. November 30. <https://vinaylal.wordpress.com/2010/11/30/thesis-two-postcolonialism-has-had-nothing-to-say-about-the-imperialism-of-categories/>. Wiley, Angela. 2016. "A World of Materialisms: Postcolonial Feminist Science Studies and the New Natural." *Science, Technology, & Human Values* 41 (6): 991–1014. doi:10.1177/0162243916658707.

Participants:

"Digital Untouchability": Convergence of smart-technology,

HR policy and architecture in reifying segregation based-upon caste *Ravikant Kisana; Nioshi Shah, University of Chicago*

Caste system within South Asia is characterised by strict rules of hierarchical social segregation. In its most extreme form, it deems the people considered 'lowest' as 'untouchable'. This is based upon conservative purity-norms among other things, as the 'lowest' castes are relegated to occupations traditionally considered to be unclean, such as sanitation work. The post-colonial Indian state legally abolished 'untouchability' but it remains deeply socially embedded, though invisibilized, especially within the contemporary urban environment. This paper seeks to study this invisible but widely prevalent untouchability based on caste within the modern Indian workspaces. We seek to draw our thesis via a case-study of the Flame University campus in Pune, India. This is an elite liberal education private university boasting of international faculty and a world-class campus. Within this space however, the dining hall of campus, neatly recreates the hierarchy of caste segregation. Air-conditioned upper tiers are only available to the upper-caste management, and basement space is kept for low caste sanitation workers. As per HR policy, food is served only after a digital fingerprint scan. The scanners in upper tiers are programmed to not register sanitation workers, hence keeping them within their 'unofficial' prescribed location. Our case study navigates the architecture and smart-tech infrastructure of the campus and tries to identify nodes of sociotechnical assemblages of caste segregation and its implications for understanding caste from a technoscience imagination.

Violence of Science and Development: Withering away of the Displaced Van Gujjars in and around Rajaji National Park, Uttarakhand, India *Prerna Sah, iFOREST; Sambit Mallick, Indian Institute of Technology Guwahati*

The proposed paper examines the displacement of forest-dwelling communities from protected areas. I study the displacement of the semi-nomadic pastoral community of the Van Gujjars from the protected area of Rajaji National Park in the state of Uttarakhand, India. The designation of the area as a national park led to the displacement and rehabilitation of the Van Gujjars, ostensibly to protect the forest from the community. However, data analysis puts forth a very ambiguous argument for the establishment of protected areas and the subsequent displacement of forest-dwelling communities. In the paper, I seek to place the displacement of the Van Gujjars within the framework of governance and development. The study carried out was based on qualitative data collection. Primary data was collected through interviews that were semi-structured. Purposive sampling was used to approach the three sets of respondents, viz. government officials, 'experts' from the Wildlife Institute of India and NGOs, and the tribal community of the Van Gujjars.

The Patidar Ethic and the Spirit of Caste: Networks of Agricultural Expertise in Rural India *Tanya Matthan*

This paper is framed around the Patidars, a peasant caste group in central and west India, well-known for their entrepreneurialism. Drawing on fieldwork in rural Malwa, I focus on narratives by and about the community in relation to their economic prosperity through commercial agriculture. Patidars are well-known for their risk-taking ventures as well as an ethic of hard work, discipline and moral virtue. I argue that capital accumulation among Patidar farmers is premised on caste and kin networks through which agricultural knowledge and expertise travels, particularly in the context of the post-liberalization shrinking of rural extension services. Theorizing caste networks as technoscientific assemblages, this paper considers the role of knowledge and expertise in the co-constitution of caste identity, rural inequality and neoliberal agrarian development.

Picking plastics 'from below': thoughts on theory-making from South Asia *Tridibesh Dey, University of Exeter*

I engage plastics and frame the futuring of plastic waste in India as an onto-methodological research position. I establish a two-way conversation highlighting exchanges between a South Asian situation and STS theory. On the one hand, I draw on the 'plasticity of care' – discussed in (Dey & Michael, in press), to illustrate how an STS grounded in complex inter-sectionalities (caste, gender, class, physical ability, religion, etc.) visibilise some of the conceptual limits of care. Care, here, being understood as a Judeo-Christian ideal of individualistic response – or response-ability – conceived as an ethico-political obligation towards a suffering other. This is not a nihilistic denial of a 'Northern' idea, rather a situated unpicking of care, re-enacting its potentials for conceptual work. Fieldwork anecdotes from a grassroots anti-plastic movement and occasions of domestic plastic repurposing in Jodhpur, Rajasthan, inform this part of the discussion 'from below', where we render care 'plastic'. On the other hand, I use Deleuzian 'assemblage' theory to 'materialize' the political economy of 'Clean India'. This draws on empirical examples from Ahmedabad. Here, plastic waste gathering and recycling practices face unfair competition from the large-scale infrastructuring of municipal solid waste management modelled around WTE (waste to energy) systems and 'informal' labour is co-opted. The socio-materialisation of Clean India presents actual patterns of plastic fixity and flow, framing these not purely as challenges to marginalised practitioners (Gidwani, 2013) but enabling alternative expressions of 'subaltern' agencies. This work echoes critical urban scholarship and relevant North-South, South-South theoretical exchanges (Ranganathan, 2015; Anand, 2017).

Session Organizers:

Misria Shaik Ali, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Prerna Srigyan, University of California - Irvine

Discussant:

anapurna mamidipudi, Max Planck Institute for the History of Science

138. Reception

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: Auditorium

Reception - Mentoring meet ups

Participant:

Reception *Vanbasten de Araujo*, University of Toronto

Reception

Session Organizer:

Vanbasten de Araujo, University of Toronto

139. (Im)material streams in the city: ecologies, economies, electrons

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Participants:

Flows of data, ecologies in resistance: The rise of data centres and water plundering in Santiago de Chile *Martin Tironi; Matías Valderrama, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Camila Albornoz*

In the last decade, there has been a "data centre fever" in Chile. Large investments are being made in the country for the creation of data centres by the Big Tech companies. In 2012, Google announced the construction of its first data centre in the southern hemisphere in the municipality of Quilicura of Santiago de Chile. This US\$150 million investment was aimed at placing Chile at the technological forefront in Latin America. In July 2019, Google filed for environmental impact assessment approval for a second \$200 million data centre in an industrial zone of the municipality of Cerrillos. This new expansion of Google services has not been without controversy. The materialities that support Google's technological infrastructure do not seem to be

resilient to the environment since 169 litres of water per second will need to be extracted for the operation of the servers. Local communities have expressed their opposition to the construction of this data centre, criticising the plundering of water in the middle of the great drought in central Chile and legal actions are underway to stop the progress of the data centre. Through a digital ethnography that crosses the sites of resistance to this data centre, press coverage as well as public debates in social media platforms, in this paper we analyse how the supposedly immaterial "cloud" has material implications on invisibilized territories. As we will show, the flows of digital data are intertwined with the opaque water market in Chile, where water rights allow private holders to extract and use specific water flow for private purposes.

(Im)Material Entanglements: Advancing Critical Engagements with our Technologically Mediated Built Environment *Maya Przybylski, University of Waterloo, Canada*

Architects are increasingly bundling digital components together with physical assemblies in their pursuit of responsive (or sentient, adaptive, interactive, smart) architecture. At the same time, we are increasingly aware that (immaterial) digital elements, such as software and data, have direct spatial, social, political, and cultural agency and, further, understanding and managing these entanglements is paramount when supporting equitable, diverse and inclusive ways to organize, use and shape the built environment. As architects build expertise in the technical aspects of SED practice, there is an opportunity, expanding on the discipline's tradition of engaging the built world from technical, social, and cultural perspectives, to support more comprehensive (socially-, ethically-, politically-minded) engagements with the technologically mediated built environment. Such work requires new forms of critical computational literacy and tools. This paper advances efforts to build this required critical computational literacy in two parts. First, through discussion around recent media studies scholarship, establishing materialist accounts of digital technology, we argue that immaterial elements, such as algorithms, data and code implementations, should not be decoupled from a project's physical dimension and instead be thought of as constituting part of the project's material assembly. This reconceptualization elevates the obligations architects have towards computational components by subjecting them to similar sociocultural considerations targeted at physical aspects of their work. The second presents ongoing work on our Project Anatomy framework aimed at simultaneously confronting projects' soft and hard materials to analyze relationships between computational components, physical materials, and real-world outcomes. The tool foregrounds SED designers' position to find new purchase on comprehensive engagements with the computational components increasingly proliferating in our built environment.

Inside/Outside: Emerging Data-driven Landscapes of Indoor Horticulture in the Netherlands *Grace Abou Jaoude, Technical University of Braunschweig; Victor Munoz Sanz, TU Delft*

Dutch controlled environment agriculture is increasingly celebrated as the future of food production—a techno-utopia that optimizes microclimatic control to address environmental pressures and radical climate change. However, the role of data-driven technologies and their socio-ecological and spatial implications remain limited in literature. We explore the phenomenon of automation in Westland, the largest greenhouse cluster in the Netherlands. We investigate the digitalization and datafication of indoor horticulture, the assemblages of hardware, software, and bodies that inhabit these spaces, and reveal the role of these infrastructures in reorganizing the urban fabric and orchestrating metabolic flows. Deriving from previous studies in urban political ecology, we map material processes in Westland's

greenhouses and their spatialization to underscore the ways in which socio-technical systems contribute to capital accumulation and urban reproduction. We present a situated analysis revealing how automation technologies and digital infrastructure reconfigure particular places while embedded within broader networks across scales. With processes of multiplication and scaling-up of greenhouses intensify the circulation of capital, precarious work and labor inequalities as well as uneven development, Westland epitomizes tensions, power relations and complexities and conceptualizes the role of capital and data in accelerating the adoption of digital technologies.

The “digital city”: co-constructing “realness” through digital infrastructures in pandemic NYC *Jordan H Kraemer, New York University Tandon School of Engineering; Mona Sloane*

This paper examines the emergence of the “digital city” in New York during the COVID-19 pandemic lockdowns of 2020. We draw on multi-sited digital ethnography across multiple platforms, technologies, and communities to explore how residents across all five boroughs--Manhattan, Queens, the Bronx, Brooklyn, and Staten Island--maintained and built social ties, creating new forms of digital practice despite social distancing mandates. In particular, we examine how people forged experiences of “real” places and how local geographies and cultures were enacted online to achieve “realness.” What counted as “real” places online was specific to different communities and social contexts, produced through the same platforms in varied and often divergent ways. Because of the pandemic lockdowns, many New York City residents spent more time in their neighborhoods, and became more involved in neighborhood organizing and mutual support, particularly in underserved areas. These practices also shaped the multiple ways locality was produced online. We argue for more careful attention to how varied communities and constituents produced the “digital city,” grounding digital practices in uneven material infrastructures, with implications for public space design and urban infrastructure policy.

Session Organizer:

Morgan Mouton, Lab'URBA/Université Gustave Eiffel

140. Critical Augmented Reality Studies: newly material forms of digital formations of identity, surveillance, and publics

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Participants:

A tale of two realities via multi-method comparison of Augmented Reality research and consumer product engagement: The best and worst of times in the AR present *luke heemsbergen, Deakin University*

Although the majority of Augmented Reality (AR) scholarship is based in Computer Science disciplines, it is nevertheless important to consider emergent trends in the AR discourse as research and development shifts from technology labs to media markets. Our argument is that while technical understandings of AR are necessary, they are insufficient to understand how spatial computing augments everyday life and we hope to document how STS can inform such shifts. This paper maps the AR discourse for nodes of power and authority in two ways. First, it systematically reviews and the ways in which AR research citations are shifting from science and technical foci to applied uses of AR, building from work of Ciproso et al. (2018). To do so it employs a discursive analysis of quantitative research citation patterns made visible via CiteSpace to identify emerging trends in AR research up to the year 2020 (n:12,328 Web of Science), to comment on how disciplinary boundaries shape how AR is understood and innovated. The paper then compares these patterns and themes to evolving public consumer perceptions of AR by systematically mapping phone-based AR apps available

on the iOS app store and Google Play market. Here we employ open coding of top available “AR” apps until saturation points. We conclude by charting future research directions based on our findings that speak to the patterns of authority and power in this rapidly growing techno-media industry.

Augmented reality, time, and visions of control *Ben Egliston, Queensland University of Technology; Marcus Carter, The University of Sydney*

This talk examines the imagination of Augmented Reality (AR) as a data-rich sensing technology, specifically engaging with discourses of time that emerge from an ongoing analysis of AR projects for i) military use (e.g., Microsoft’s collaboration with the US military to develop an Integrated Visual Augmentation System Program) and ii) for the governance of urban civil society (e.g., the growing industry of AR for biometric tracking post-COVID-19). The first part of this talk shows how AR is commonly framed as a powerful tool for generating data (about the body, the environment etc) and rendering data (e.g., through linkage to surveillance databases) visible to human perception through its interface. We argue that this data-richness was commonly framed around a temporal affordance – of shaping the perception of the user in ways that, in line with the dominant security and military doctrines of the West, target, classify and pre-empt potential threat. The second part of our talk discusses the social and political values that emerge in these framings of AR’s technicity, and the urgency in challenging the faulty if not fraudulent logics on which much of the AR imaginary is based.

Is it Time for an Augmented Reality Theory? Synthesizing Existing Theoretical Frameworks to Better Guide Research into AR *Tony Liao, University of Houston*

Oftentimes with emerging technologies like augmented reality (AR), early research takes two paths. The first is where researchers believe the novel technology is so unique that exploratory, iterative research is necessary to understand it at a basic level. These studies tend to use the technology as a wholesale stand-in for several variables, and have offered important findings that AR technology had certain effects, but without necessarily understanding the underlying mechanisms for why or how AR led to those outcomes. The second path is to draw on existing theories that are related to the emerging technologies, and explain how the technology builds our understanding of those theories. With AR, scholars have drawn on psychological perception theories, CMC/cues/presence theories, locative spatial theories, interactivity theories, human computer interaction/human machine communication theories, visual theories, media effects theories, technological adoption theories, just to name a few. These studies are similarly important for grounding the technology in existing theory, but they may be limited in how it understands only one component of AR technology and also bound to the traditions and limitations of the theory itself. Through a systematic review of the AR literature, this study attempts to merge research from these two perspectives to construct a theory matrix for understanding AR. In doing so, we hope to map the existing area in a more productive way while also guiding researchers toward combinations of theories that could help better understand AR as a specific technology and potentially yield AR specific theories.

Situating Augmented Reality in Construction Work: An Analysis of Commercial Videos and User Imaginations *Ann-Kathrin Wortmeier, Universität Stuttgart*

Augmented reality (AR) technologies such as AR glasses are currently in development for industrial applications, including construction work, promising to simplify complex tasks (Kim et al. 2016). AR technologies are often presented as a possible remedy to the skilled worker shortage in construction. Research laboratories and IT companies envision future users and the required skills for handling AR technologies. Companies rely on commercial videos to promote future use in the construction

sector. An analysis of commercial videos on industrial AR technologies shows how these and their users are situated within techno-euphoric promises and specific user representations. Tasked with gathering information on actual use cases, user needs, and characteristics, designers create specific ideas of user worlds (Akrich 1992; Fischer et al. 2020). The analysis reveals that different subtexual promises of AR technologies, such as cost/time savings, an oversimplification of work processes, and limited workers' training, prevail. Perceived as experts in situ, AR construction work users can efficiently solve problems through new learning strategies and information visualization. In contrast, the expectation is that special knowledge and training might become obsolete. These two commercially-driven images indicate a re-negotiation of skilled workers using intelligent wearable technologies. The paper argues that future AR users' conceptualizations and the actual required skills for human-technology collaboration deviate by combining the video analysis with results from fieldwork in the German timber prefabrication sector. Incorporating wearable AR technologies in construction work creates new human entanglements with technology and "new forms of knowledge about the world" (Akrich 1992: 207).

Technological corporeal worlds with exoskeletal devices *Denisa Butnaru, University of Konstanz*

The tradition of the grounded theory methodology (GTM) is well known for the concept of "social world" (Strauss 1978; 1991; Clarke 1998: 265). Although Anselm Strauss acknowledges a certain preference of this category for universes of discourse, he also notes that "we should be careful not to confine ourselves to looking merely at forms of communication, symbolization, and universes of discourses, but also examine palpable matters like activities, memberships, sites, technologies, and organizations typical of particular social worlds" (Strauss 1991: 219). Starting from this conception, my intention is in this presentation to discuss the emergence of "corporeal worlds" shaped by such novel technologies as exoskeletal devices. Exoskeletons are gadgets developed for three areas: rehabilitation, industry and military. The type of corporeal needs and support they address is highly determined by the definitions of these three worlds, which I understand, differently from Strauss' perspective, to be mainly practice oriented. The primary reality of our bodies is that of their situating us, and thus of contributing to shape situations. If bodies are transformed by technologies, so are their situations and by extension, the very worlds they compose. While using the categorical heritage from the contemporary phenomenology of the body and embodiment, more specifically enactivism (Gallagher 2012; 2017), I will give an overview of how exoskeletons, besides specific capabilities, abilities and skills, shape unprecedented corporeal worlds while contributing to foster unique alterity forms.

The AR Cloud: Tech Imaginaries, Future Risks, and Potential Affordances *Andrew Iliadis, Temple University; Isabel Pedersen, Ontario Tech University; Ann Hill Duin, University of Minnesota; Liron Efrat, Ontario Tech University*

After undergoing 20 years of emergence, Augmented Reality (AR) is predicted to progress to become a full-scale ambient platform. AR is a method of human-computer interaction that blends virtual representations with physical spaces, seeking to augment, mix, or shift reality (Azuma, 1997). This presentation uses a digital repository of artifacts about this technology at <https://fabricofdigitallife.com> (Fabric) to explore the prediction that AR will evolve to become an ambient computing platform, and to shed light on both potential risks and affordances. The transformative quality of AR is that it combines virtual components with human sensory modalities (e.g., sight, sound, touch), meaning that it can augment the first-person point of view of the user with the potential to achieve a significant sense of virtual presence. Analysis of key artifacts in Fabric illustrates the

next iteration of Augmented Reality, the 'AR Cloud' or 'Mirrorworld,' as a speculative plan to create a shared multi-user environment, a global augmented reality, and "a real time spatial map of the world" (Inbar, 2018; Kelly, 2019). For example, the AR cloud requires a persistent 3D digital copy of the world, which means that if a developer creates a virtual overlay for a real space, it will remain accessible to anyone across different devices and platforms. As an imagined technology future, this presentation addresses how AR could affect both positive societal change (e.g., Open AR Cloud Association) as well as result in greater risk through further conditions of surveillance, corporate control, or harms to humans.

Session Organizer:

luke heemsbergen, Deakin University

141. Bias, Risk, and Opacity in Machine Learning Algorithms

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

This panel explores the role of bias, risk and opacity in machine learning technologies. Papers consider the development of parole request tools, theorize the generation of bias in machine learning algorithms, and consider the status of algorithmic opacity for both programmers and users alike.

Participants:

Assessing Biases, Relaxing Moralism: On Ground-Truthing Practices in Machine Learning Design and Application *Florian Jatton, STS Lab, University of Lausanne*

This theoretical paper considers the morality of machine learning (ML) algorithms and systems in the light of the biases that ground their correctness. It begins by presenting biases not as a priori negative entities but as contingent external referents – often gathered in benchmarked repositories called ground-truth datasets – that both define what needs to be learned and allow for performance measures. I then argue that ground-truth datasets and their concomitant practices – that fundamentally involve establishing biases to enable learning procedures – can be described by their respective morality, here defined as the more-or-less accounted experience of hesitation when faced with what pragmatist philosopher William James called "genuine options" (1912) – that is, choices to be made in the heat of the moment that engage different possible futures. I then stress three constitutive dimensions of this pragmatist morality, as far as ground-truthing practices are concerned: I) the definition of the problem to be solved (problematization); II) the identification of the data to be collected and set up (databasing); and III) the qualification of the targets to be learned (labeling). I finally suggest that this three-dimensional conceptual space can be used to map ML algorithmic projects in terms of the morality of their respective and constitutive ground-truthing practices. Such techno-moral graphs may, in turn, serve as equipment for greater governance of ML algorithms and systems.

Predicting Crime Risk: The Development Of Risk Assessment Tools in the US *Iara Passos, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS/Brasil)*

In 1920s actuarial tools began to be implemented in the evaluation of parole requests in order to predict or estimate the possible recidivism of the benefit's applicants in the USA. Since then, they have been used to better manage the population under correctional control, offered by state or private companies, calculating the individuals' risk of recidivism, who have violent behaviour or failure to appear in the court, from factors like: criminal history, age, marital status, sex, and behavioral, based on criminological theories and machine learning techniques. The necessity to predict a future recidivism has directly impacted the way institutions think and deal with criminal law enforcement. This tools are based in forms application and the choice of its questions impacts the risk factors' definition. Nowadays, there are more than 400 tools

being use in different phases of the US criminal justice system, among states, counties and national jurisdictions, mainly after the increase of the criticism against the bail system and the criminal justice bias. This paper analyse 24 tools' forms used by jurisdictions of the USA, from a STS and content analysis perspective. The main results are that tools focus in a specific kind of suspect — poor and black people, because they target housing, neighborhood, scholar and employment history, drugs/alcohol issues — since its conception and development, even if the companies and government agencies argued that they are neutral and objective.

History without stories: problems of algorithmic opacity for historical interpretation *Ethan Hallerman, Stony Brook University*

Algorithmic opacity is usually addressed with an eye toward ameliorating lay discomfort with non-agential decision-making, often through proposals for improved science communication. Such concerns recall familiar tensions between democratic decision-making and the authority of expertise or bureaucracies, in which the latter threaten subjects' capacities for agency and imagination. However, while these concerns remain relevant, determinations made via machine learning algorithms differ qualitatively from older forms of automated judgement: a machine learning algorithm may in key ways be opaque even to programmers, because it may not operate according to an intuitively graspable logic. The problem here is similar to, and connected to, the disregard of big-data analysis for causal explanation: just as big data's correlative accounts preclude a narrative structure that meaningfully links the past to the future, decisions whose logic is inaccessible in principle would render the consequences of those decisions beyond interpretation. Algorithmic opacity thus poses a novel problem: how are the possibilities for politics and for the interpretation of experience narrowed when social issues (or their causes) are no longer phenomenologically or hermeneutically accessible? This question should be framed in the terms of the debate between hermeneutics and empiricism concerning the relationship of interpretation and explanation. In *The Open Society and Its Enemies*, Karl Popper defended a non-hermeneutic account of history that would bring it closer to the operations of the natural sciences. For Popper, since intentions cannot truly explain outcomes, they should not be used in historical explanation. Today, when agency and intent may be simply uninvolved in decision-making, and may have no place in descriptions of the future, the debate between empiricism and hermeneutics will be resolved practically rather than theoretically.

Criticism And Prophecy In Media Coverage Of AI Controversies *Maxime Crépel, FNSP; Dominique Cardon, Sciences Po*

Using various methods of natural language processing on a large corpus of press articles covering a period of 5 years, we show two dominant regimes of criticism of artificial intelligence that coexist within the media sphere, involving different technological and human entities, but also distinct temporality and issues. We observe a shift between articles featuring algorithmic calculation techniques incorporated into the user's environment to guide, orient or calculate his behaviors, towards articles characterized by a personification of AI in an embodied and autonomous entity. This topology can be interpreted as a process of progressive independence of AI that constitutes a constant polarity in the history of the relationship between computer technology and society. On the one hand, robots and AI, which refer to autonomous and embodied technical entities, are associated with a prophetic discourse alerting on the capacity to control these agents that simulate our physical and cognitive capacities and threaten our physical security or our economic model. This regime of critical enunciation is organized around the feeling of fear regarding the autonomy of robots, which thrives on science fiction, religious concerns and contains a

prophetic dimension on the future of humanity. On the other hand, the technical entities are represented by algorithms that shape our daily computing environments. They are associated with a short term discourse, focusing on populations characterized by their age, ethnicity, political or sexual orientation, and mobilizing a social justice criticism that denounce bias, discrimination, surveillance, censorship and amplification in the diffusion of inappropriate content.

Session Organizer:

Florian Jatton, STS Lab, University of Lausanne

142. Fleshing out the Digital: Exploring heterogenous bodies and relationality in digitalized worlds

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

In its imagined and actual dimensions, the fourth industrial revolution blurs the lines between the physical, the digital and the biological. This panel explores the ways in which bodies, identities and relations exceed the confines of the digital – non-digital binary and how relations are made (im)possible in their excess. What happens when we force organic matter(s) into digital molds and models? How does the excess interact with the frame, and how can flesh and bodies – individual and collective – reactivate claims of sovereignty and rights in world that is, despite utopian claims, more-than-digital? We approach digitalization as a recolonization of thought and practice, and ask how might we grasp these relations at a time when the deconstruction of epistemological binaries is well underway? The digital here refers to the pervasive global and historically specific movement to reform basic societal relations and functions, such as economic transactions, healthcare, welfare services, the provision of basic physical resources (e.g. water and electricity), security, and the negotiation of social identities through AI and automation. Despite the utopian promise of better services and care for all through digitalization, these technologies seem only to amplify the gap between those who enjoy care and those who suffer neglect. We invite papers that, through STS approaches and practices, make room for relations otherwise by taking digital logics seriously as empirical objects in which more-than-digital relations unfold in and spill over their digital confines.

Participants:

How Information Gains Its Bodies *Ana Viseu, IADE - Universidade Europeia; Jacinthe Flore, RMIT*

In 1999, Hayles famously argued that “information had lost its body” to describe how information had become understood as being separate from the matter and materials that instantiate it. In this paper, we continue to examine this loss by focusing on two wearable and sensory artefacts seemingly designed for fitness and lifestyle changes, namely Naked by Naked Labs and Amazon's Halo Band. The drive towards the use of wearable technology for these purposes is not new, and neither is the claim that using them renders visible previously inaccessible bodily-knowledge (Viseu 2005). What distinguishes these devices is that they require users to strip down to their underwear, take pictures, and then proceed to create 3-D body models — in what the Washington Post has described as “the most invasive tech we've ever tested” (referring to Halo). Our analysis draws upon the methodology proposed by Flore and Piennar (2020) whereby we deploy an analysis of the websites of these two devices, as well as other publicly available data. By examining these two technological devices we are interested in understanding not only the promissory discourses that encourage users to feel a need (or an advantage) in having such 3-D models, but also what functionalities are deemed to be important (or not), and finally, the sociotechnical worlds these technologies work to enact. We are particularly concerned with how these bodies that are now gained by the information, coexist and feed into what Zubboff (2019) has termed “surveillance capitalism”.

"Making Up" Biometric Personhood: Digital Addressing and the Construction of Citizenship in Ghana *Alena Thiel, Martin Luther University Halle-Wittenberg*

The now well-established debate on biometric technology adoption in the so-called Global South has centred predominantly on techno-optimist promises around the universal inclusion of previously undocumented populations (Gelb and Clark 2013). Surprisingly little attention has been paid to how the automation of biometric identification and its applications in data-driven governance have impacted the construction of personhood. Drawing on the now classic theory of Hacking's "human kinds" as well as the social study of quantification in more general terms, this paper explores the infrastructural decisions that went into mobilizing biometric data doubles on new kinds of "data journeys" (Lemov 2017) between previously isolated population registers in Ghana. Interoperable population data infrastructuring, my interviews and observations involving various Ghanaian data users and producers show, targets the integration of biometric, administrative and geospatial data from state, financial and telecommunication records. Data logics supporting this transformation largely follow the model of the Scandinavian population data system as a "travelling concept" along with its inscribed "protocols for intervention" (Behrends, Park and Rottenburg 2014). The paper zooms in on the performative nature of population data by focusing on the spatial fix of official personhood in Ghana's biometrically-linked, GPS-based addressing system. Although democratizing in lowering the threshold for registration through app-based interfaces and institutional representation in remote areas of the country, the retroactive (Desrosières 2015) effects on the categories of personhood this infrastructural arrangement is supposed to datify so far remain elusive. The paper raises the question how notions of access, inclusion and entitlement are affected by emerging technological transformations in the context of nascent welfare systems in illustrating how interoperable population registers participate in the construction of new categories of personhood in relation to taxation and state service delivery.

Placing (Future) Care: Exploring More Than-Digital-Relations In Digital Care Spaces *Dara Ivanova, Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management; Thorben Peter Simonsen, IT University Copenhagen*

Science and technology studies scholars have considered the multiple socio-technical relations between place and care, concerning themselves with how one is integral to the other in different care settings. With the spread of digitalization, however, the spaces of health/care are fundamentally changing. In this paper, we examine two cases of using virtual reality in healthcare provision from the Netherlands and Denmark and seek to develop conceptual means for better understanding what 'digital care spaces' might be, how – and for whom – they might make a difference, and how they reimagine 'good care'. These empirical cases illustrate that re-placing care to digital spaces produces more-than-digital relations by which bodies become emplaced in novel ways with particular consequences. Building on previous ethnographic work on the nature of space and placed care (Ivanova 2020, Simonsen 2020), we propose that the concepts place-by-proxy and post-place care will be helpful for theorizing how spatial relations between bodies, the digital, and practices of care are being reconfigured. These concepts foreground and problematize the notion of place and its relationship to digitalization in healthcare. Leveraging them to understand how virtual reality is being applied within healthcare in two countries, we further suggest that digital care spaces instigate new ethical dilemmas in emerging digital care infrastructures.

Should I Provide My Digital Health Data For Research? - Citizens' Registers Of (E)valuation And Justification *Susanne Oechsner, University of Vienna; Robin Rae, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies; Luca Lindner, University of Vienna; Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies*

At a moment in time when the importance of big data has moved high on the agenda, dealing responsibly with them poses an important dilemma: on the one hand, there is a clear argument in favor of providing data for research in the name of collective health care benefits; on the other hand, there are concerns that people might lose the sovereignty over their data. While there is a broad debate about these issues, our contribution wants to investigate in a more fine-grained manner the situated ways in which citizens reflect, assess and justify the (non)provision of their digitally available health records for research. Empirically, this paper draws on ongoing engagements with potential citizen users of a health data platform in the making, in the Horizon2020 project Smart4Health (Grant Number 826117). The functionalities of the platform comprise collecting, managing and sharing a diverse set of health(-related) data, with the option of also providing data for research. We will use data from testing the informed consent process with citizens, which provided detailed insights into their reflections, valuations, assessments and justifications. Our approach offers vivid insights into citizens' situated (1) understanding of data, (2) underlying assumptions of "just returns" for their contribution, (3) visions of good and trustworthy governance, (4) imaginations of potential data journeys to (in)acceptable locations, (5) projections of potential health futures and (6) perceptions of risks and responsibilities.

Tele-expertise as a remote practice that reorganizes face-to-face care *Dilara Vanessa TRUPIA, Inserm; Alexandre MATHIEU-FRITZ, University of Gustave Eiffel*

Tele-expertise (TLX) is a particular form of health care practice in which a physician, known as the "requesting", solicits the remote opinion of another practitioner, known as the "requested", by sharing with him/her clinical information and photographic elements that he/she produces for this purpose. From one perspective, TLX is an excellent example of digitization of the doctor/patient relationship where digitized information and photos replace direct interaction. However, TLX is also developing as a new framework whose purpose is not necessarily to replace the traditional face-to-face consultations, but to reconfigure care pathways according to the accessibility of specialists and the gravity of certain pathologies. This contribution proposes presenting the unique way in which TLX practices are developed in the case of dermatology. It is based on a survey conducted through semi-directive interviews with about fifteen dermatologists practicing TLX within a university hospital in the French metropolitan area, which hosts emergencies and is a reference center for certain rare pathologies in dermatology. This contribution will show how TLX produces ambivalent recomposition effects: when it allows specialists in metropolitan areas to select face-to-face consultations, TLX can also avoid the travel of some patients who are in medical deserts, without however solving their problem. In this respect, while TLX makes it possible to avoid consultations deemed non-urgent, it can also help improve the preparation of face-to-face consultations. It is through STS approaches that we will show how TLX is developing both as a new practice for producing remote diagnostic advice and as a tool for organizing face-to-face consultations.

Session Organizer:

Adrienne Mannov, Aarhus University

Chair:

Carolina Sanchez Boe, Aarhus University

Discussant:

Astrid Andersen, Aalborg University

143. Semiosis in the Lab: Translating the Language of Practising Scientists

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

One of the barriers to communicating effective scientific practice and policy to the general public is the difference in the registers spoken by scientists and members of the general public. When this gap between the scientific 'empiricist' register and the everyday 'contingent' register remains large, it can lead to cynicism, uncertainty, and at worst, distrust and fear amongst nonspecialists (Gilbert & Mulkay 1984). The fields of linguistic anthropology, sociolinguistics, pragmatics, and sociology, amongst others have attended to different aspects of 'semiosis in the lab' through such varied methodologies as participant-observation (Traawek 1988; Forsythe 2001), semi-structured interviews (Gilbert & Mulkay 1984; Martin 1987), body language (Ochs et al. 1996; Hao & Hood 2017), conversation analysis and ethnomethodology (Goodwin 2018; Lynch 1993), historical discourse analysis (Hesse 1980, 1966; Brown 2003; Collins & Pinch 2012), poetics (Bielo 2019), and critical metaphor analysis (Black 2018; Martin 1987). In order to develop and maintain 'good relations' between practising scientists and the public, social scientists have a role to play in 'translating' the process of semiosis in the laboratory (or wherever scientists practice their trade), into registers that are accessible to a wider audience (Satsuka 2015). This panel will assemble scholars performing research at the intersection between language, semiotics and science studies, specifically in the analysis of semiosis in real-time research situations instead of in highly mediated forms such as formal papers or science textbooks.

Participants:

Linguistic practices and representations of Argentinian scientists *Lucia Cespedes, Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios sobre Cultura y Sociedad (CONICET-UNC)*

The influence and role of languages and language use in an increasingly internationalized scientific field has been a matter of interdisciplinary debate over the last decades. While the issue and its many ramifications have been amply studied in settings such as multilingual higher education and research institutions in the USA, Europe, or Asia, Latin America is still underrepresented in the literature. Therefore, in this presentation we show the results of a survey on linguistic practices and representations conducted in four National Scientific and Technical Research Council (CONICET) units located in Córdoba, Argentina. While the survey analyzed 14 interrelated variables such as accumulation of linguistic capital, internationalization of trajectories, and strategies for multilingual reading and writing, among others, we will focus on the lived experiences and perceptions of agents towards the current conditions of the scientific linguistic market. A series of exploratory interviews with a sample of the surveyed population, conducted previous to the application of the questionnaire, are also part of the analytical corpus. Comparisons and contrasts are established across disciplines (Astronomy, Biomedical sciences, Law, and Humanities) and stages in the informants' academic trajectories (doctoral students, postdocs, and full-time researchers).

Peirce's argument for the multimodality of science: the continuity of semiosis *Alin Olteanu, RWTH Aachen University*

I argue that a key to making scientific practice more accessible to the public is communicating science through nonlinguistic means. Simplifying theoretical (meta)language is a lofty endeavor, where possible at all. This suggests the need for the cultivation of forms of literacy that, contrary to modern education, are not language-centered. This argument, I explain, is implicit in Charles S. Peirce's notion of semiosis. Peirce explicated this, albeit in the philosophical terminology of the time. The actuality of this notion is made evident by the correlating emergence of new forms of literacy that correspond to the modalities of new digital media and the increase in interest for Peirce's semiotics. Following Peirce, semiosis starts from intuition, which is abductive, and further proceeds with deduction and induction. Contrary to positivism, Peirce considered that, while not linguistic, abduction is essential for scientific inquiry. Deduction and induction require abduction

throughout the inferential process. The stages of inference correspond to those of scientific inquiry: mathematics (abductive), coenosopic (deductive) and idiosopic (inductive, laboratory). Mathematics is abductive because it consists in operations with graphs, which do not require a specialized (meta-)language. The nonlinguistic expression of a hypothesis is retained throughout scientific inquiry. While modern science aims to convey its results in formal and natural languages, these can also be conveyed nonlinguistically, through graphs. Popularizing scientific practices in graphs requires an effort from both academia and primary education to cultivate new literacies that do not center on linguistic expression. The emergence of digital media both demands and facilitates this.

Seeking Consensus: The Rhetoric of Lyme Disease in Canada
Loren Gaudet, University of Victoria

This paper is part of a larger project that seeks to map how Lyme disease in Canada, specifically chronic Lyme, has been understood, categorized, and experienced. Much of the research on Lyme Disease in Canada focuses on the treatment and prevention in clinical and public health settings. What I wish to contribute with this project is to explore the processes of knowledge-production, knowledge-translation, and knowledge-mobilization in relation to Lyme Disease. In this paper, I focus specifically on The Conference to develop a federal framework on Lyme disease (2016) and the public discourse that surrounded this conference. I specifically attend to the types of scientific accommodation that took place: how was scientific material from the previous 5 years utilized and translated into conference proceedings and again to the broader public(s)? What were the terms of dispute? Using the rhetorical concept of Kairos, or the fitness of conditions to bring about a particular situation, I analyze the rhetorical circumstances that prompted a consensus conference in 2016. In order to gain a better understanding of what prompted the need for consensus in Canada around Lyme disease, I compare scientific journals with a survey of Canadian Newspapers to provide a selection of national attitude and scope. Lyme disease is an ideal site for research in health communication: as it exemplifies how diseases and diagnostic criteria emerge and are shaped by national boundaries, scientific and public communities, and social and historical contexts, as well as how these categories are taken up, rejected, circulated, and revisited.

Who Are Eligible to Communicate Science? Struggle for Legitimate Role as Science Communicators Between the Public and Scientists *Zheng Yang, The University of Sheffield*

With the development of the public engagement with science, the scope of science that public are eligible to participate has been gradually expanded, from the public discussion of scientific affairs, science and technology policy formulation, scientific knowledge production to the public communication of science. The public, represented by citizen science communicators, actively participate in the science communication process, as the role of communicators rather than active audiences, in the digital media environment. However, without professional scientific background, whether the legitimacy of those public as communicators, participating in online science communication process, is recognized by scientists and other members of the public is still a question that remains to be studied. This study first explored the current situation of citizen science communicators in online digital media environment, taking the genetically modified food discussion on Zhihu as example, using the method of online ethnography. This study then interviewed 24 active users (12 scientists, 12 non-scientists) of the genetically modified food section on Zhihu and analyzed their perceptions of the legality of the role of science communicators played by scientists and the public in online genetically modified food discussion. The interview results show that both scientists and the public are trying to prove their legitimacy as science communicators in online science communication process; the

authority of scientists as science communicators has begun to be questioned by the public; and scientists try to prove the 'irrationality' of the public as science communicators from different perspectives, then maintaining their own discourse authority as communicators in online science communication process.

Session Organizer:

Joseph Wilson, University of Toronto

Chair:

Joseph Wilson, University of Toronto

144. Responding to the Challenge of Relevance: Taking Philosophy into the Field

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Pandemic-driven disruption of university life has increased pressure on academics to demonstrate their wider relevance to society. A movement known as Field Philosophy constitutes a new way to practice STS and philosophy in public venues. Field philosophy expands the range of philosophical activity, reaching beyond the classroom to directly respond to societal needs. Field philosophers apply classical theories and analytic skills in hospitals and labs, offices and community centers, cornfields and wilderness areas. They employ a variety of tools to achieve their goals: sticky notes, computer models, games, and even a hand lens. Working in settings where pressing decisions hang in the balance, and with collaborators from all walks of life, field philosophers identify the philosophical aspects of problems as they arise in messy, pressing, real-world settings. This approach returns to the original impetus of STS, which sought to make a difference in the wider world. This panel offers five accounts of academic philosophers who have taken philosophy into the field, followed by one discussant. Panelists recount both their successes and failures, and also draw out lessons learned so others can be more effective in their efforts at public philosophy with STEM-related projects. The discussant will summarize the commonalities and differences in the presented approaches to philosophical fieldwork and invite the presenters and audience participants to explore the challenges and opportunities that field philosophy raises, given common assumptions about traditional philosophical scholarship.

Participants:

Sustainability: What Everyone Needs to Know *Paul Thompson*, Michigan State University

This presentation will discuss my collaboration with Patricia Norris, a natural resource economist, in developing a foundations course on sustainability for Michigan State University's environmental studies program and writing a book intended for a general audience entitled Sustainability: What Everyone Needs to Know. I will highlight three moments in the collaboration where field philosophy was practiced. First, my work on sustainability paradigms helped frame the goals of our collaboration, though this idea was ultimately sublimated in the final product. It was not what everyone needed to know. Second, my study of a field philosopher from the previous generation, C. West Churchman, gave me a model for my own activity. Finally, a contribution on the point of environmental indicators helped Norris structure some of her own contributions to the project.

Embedding ethics in neurotechnology development *sara goering, university of washington; eran klein, university of washington*

In this presentation, we report on a qualitative interview study of neuroscientists and engineers in the NSF-funded UW Center for Neurotechnology, evaluating a nine-year collaboration with our philosophy-based embedded ethics team. Respondents saw the ethics group as a metaphorical "guiding light," a way of developing a culture where "you're expected to consider ethics before you do anything, really" and a method to ensure attention to real human needs ("as engineers, we tend to forget about people until the device is built"). We share researcher perspectives on how embedding ethics worked, why it was

valuable, and what could be done better.

The Governance of AI Technologies *Merel Noorman, Tilburg Institute for Law, Technology and Society*

This presentation will discuss the role of field philosophers in shaping the embedding and governance of AI technologies in practice. It will examine this role in the context of two AI governance clinics organized for a Dutch municipality, with the aim of helping smart city projects address ethical and social issues that go beyond the formal legal and policy questions. One key aim of the clinics was to translate abstract ethical values and guidelines, as promoted by the municipality, to the governance structures around existing practices, in particular with regard to the design and use of crowd-management systems in response to the COVID restrictions.

Engineering Ethics in the Field *J Britt Holbrook, New Jersey Institute of Technology*

This presentation discusses an experiment in field philosophy as pedagogy. In collaboration with an engineer, an ethnographer, and a community member, the author is redesigning the Engineering Ethics class he teaches to incorporate a field exercise in social justice. Key questions to be addressed include: (1) why incorporate issues of social justice into an Engineering Ethics class? (2) Why use a field exercise to teach students about engineering and social justice? The author will outline the class, with special attention to the field exercise, and discuss ways in which the team is attempting to evaluate the exercise.

Translational Ethics for Humane Tech *Margaret Little, Ethics Lab, Georgetown University; Jonathan Healey, Georgetown University; Sydney Luken*

Ethics Lab is a team of philosophers and designers that helps partners find ethical pathways in complex contexts. Here, we outline our work with the Inter-American Development Bank—the leading source of international development financing and technical assistance for Latin America and the Caribbean. Our partnership focused on proposed AI systems for a national employment program and integrated service programs for women's empowerment. Working with IADB program leaders, Ethics Lab used design methodology and exercises to surface and discuss granular, key ethical considerations implicit to IADB's projects in order to inform development of organization-wide ethical guidance for AI tools.

Session Organizers:

Robert Frodeman, Independent researcher
Evelyn Brister, Rochester Institute Of Technology

Chair:

Robert Frodeman, Independent researcher

Discussant:

Evelyn Brister, Rochester Institute Of Technology

145. Neoliberalism-focused STS Scholarship and Education in Science & Technology

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Science and Technology Studies (STS) scholars have documented and theorized how networks of living and nonliving things are produced and ensnared in global material-semiotic networks that prioritize neoliberal capitalist values like possessive individualism, continuous growth and cost externalization (Springer, Birch & MacLeavy, 2016). Such relations appear highly problematic, enriching few individuals while most others' lives are made more precarious and (a)biotic environments are rapidly degrading - threatened by existential crises like climate disruption and nuclear war (Ripple et al., 2020), along with ongoing harms like diseases from manufactured foods, privacy losses from surveillance systems and illnesses from environmental pollution. Given significant roles played by fields of science and technology in such harms, along with governments' frequent struggles to address them, educators have prominent roles to play in broadening students' understanding of apparently-problematic material-

semiotic relationships involving science and technology and in preparing them to engage in critical and proactive citizenship to help improve relations in myriad contexts (Omura et al., 2019). In this panel, science education researchers from three countries discuss analyses and uses of STS claims for exploring educational goals and approaches that may help communities thrive. The first presentation highlights critical discourse analyses of scientists' and educators' public claims regarding the CoViD-19 pandemic in Latin America. Three presentations then discuss education of secondary school students about several important STS-related concepts, such as sociotechnical imaginaries, that may help them engage more critically and proactively in relevant decisions sociopolitical. The panel finishes with discussions of university-based student-teachers' negotiation of bio-political injustices.

Participants:

Environmental Vulnerability, Risk and the Covid-19 Pandemic

María Angélica Mejía-Cáceres, Federal Rural University of Pernambuco; Humberto Martins, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro; Isabel Martins, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro

Throughout 2020, we have identified a number of texts that articulate aspects of the environmental crisis with the outbreak of the Covid-19 pandemic and its unequal impacts on human and environmental well-being throughout the world. In the case of Latin American countries, sociodemographic statistics by multilateral organizations and developmental aid agencies suggest that inequality is strongly connected to variables such as social level, gender, age, ethnic and racial condition, territory and environmental vulnerability. The consideration of sociopolitical dimensions of risk is, therefore, an important aspect of environmental education, if we are to problematise both environmental inequality and environmental justice. In this panel, we will present a critical discursive analysis of eight public online lectures by environmental scientists and environmental educators that address the connection between patterns emergence and dissemination of the SARS-Cov2 virus and aspects of the management of the pandemic in different Latin American countries. Results discuss connections between aspects of the pandemic and environmental issues such as deforestation, urban development, precarious work conditions, unhealthy housing conditions, amongst others. The analyses highlight ambivalences toward science as being connected to both causes and solutions of problems and the difficulties in communicating science about matters of public concern. They reveal ways through which conjunctural aspects, such as market interests, social exclusion and cultural prejudices, are textually realised and recontextualised in the debate. Implications for developing curriculum approaches involving relationships among fields of science and technology and societies and environments are discussed.

Pedagogical Encounters with STS through 'STEPWISE' Sarah

El Halwany; Majd Zouda, OISE, University of Toronto; John Lawrence Bencze, Ontario Institute for Studies in Education, University of Toronto

It is argued that STS scholars appear to refrain from engaging with school science on grounds of its interests in 'ready-made' science (e.g., science laws and concepts), which might be incongruent with STS's larger interests in 'science in the making' (Weinstein, 2008). 'STEPWISE' (Bencze, 2017) is a science education project that tries to challenge such perceptions of school science. STEPWISE, as an activist-oriented pedagogy, embraces teaching science in action (as socially and politically embedded) and for action (as students take actions to address various social and environmental harms related to technoscience applications). In this paper, we outline pedagogical affordances of various STS notions in further enriching STEPWISE-like approaches. We reviewed academic articles in the following STS journals: *Social Studies of Science*, *Science as Culture* and *Science, Technology and Human Values* (2010-2020). We

conducted a thematic analysis (Patton, 2002), focusing on issues related to '(bio)political economies of science and technology' (Birch, 2013). Of interest are "ways science (or knowledge of the natural world) is embedded, embodied, and enacted in particular political conditions" (Freitas et al., 2017, p. 553). Notions from STS highlighted in this paper include: 'sociotechnical imaginaries', 'emotive actants', 'anthropocentric temporalities' and 'regulatory capture'. We discuss how such notions from STS could have implications for how we teach students about fields of technoscience in relation to values, emotions, materiality, and futures. Using STEPWISE as our pedagogical anchor, we hope to appeal to STS scholars interested in ways to explicitly teach students about such notions.

Micro-Applications of Sociotechnical Imaginary and Actor Network Theory in a Science Classroom: Possibilities and Limitations *Majd Zouda, OISE, University of Toronto; Sarah El Halwany; Dimitris Tsoubaris, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens; John Lawrence Bencze, Ontario Institute for Studies in Education, University of Toronto*

To address problems related to rapid developments in technoscience, some critical voices in science education have been advocating teaching and learning science for active citizenships. However, taking effective socio-political actions, as informed citizens, requires critical and realistic understanding of technoscience (and related problems) as socio-material constructs. This includes, but is not limited to, unequal power relations, underlying moral and ethical considerations, and roles of non-human in shaping these developments and problems. Changing problematic technoscience realities might also be enriched by imagining and negotiating alternative futures through networks of socio-material relations. This paper reports on experiences of a high-school science teacher in Greece bringing together two closely-related STS concepts (i.e., Sociotechnical Imaginary and Actor Network Theory), while implementing an activist science education framework in his courses. These two macro concepts were 'simplified' and translated into the micro-realities of science classroom through values negotiation processes and active engagement in imagining alternative futures. While examining different technoscience commodities and their related socioscientific issues, students tended to construct 'micro-sociotechnical imaginaries' and negotiated their prioritized values, and possible values of other stakeholders. They also created Actor Network-based mind maps that represented their evolving learning and negotiation processes. Our research indicates possible merits of micro-applications of these concepts in enabling students to construct visions for how they lead their lives. It also suggests possible approaches to practically engage students and support them to develop meaningful understanding of these usually complex concepts. Limitations of these approaches are also discussed.

Secondary School Science Students Imagining Dispositifs Prioritizing Their Educated and Research-informed Ideologies Regarding Possibly-problematic Material-Semiotic Relationships *John Lawrence Bencze, Ontario Institute for Studies in Education, University of Toronto; Dave Del Gobbo, Peel District School Board; Sarah El Halwany; Minja Milanovic, Ontario Institute for Studies in Education, University of Toronto; Nurul Hassan Mohammad, OISE, University of Toronto; Jasmine Yeung, OISE, University of Toronto; Majd Zouda, OISE, University of Toronto*

Much of our world seems precarious. There are fears, for instance, that humanity is on a 'precipice' due to threats from climate change, habitat destruction and species losses, nuclear weaponry and more. Meanwhile, societies appear plagued by ongoing struggles like those to eliminate diseases (e.g., cancer) from manufactured foods, privacy and autonomy threats from

surveillance systems, and harms from prescription and illicit drugs. Associated with many such harms are fields of science and technology (S&T). However, research claims from Science and Technology Studies (STS) and related fields suggest that myriad biotic, abiotic and symbolic entities ('actants') — including fields of S&T — are interwoven, particularly under neoliberal influences, into extensive network relations (dispositifs) that largely promote capitalist goals like individual competitiveness, costs externalization and continuous growth. In this light, fields of S&T education seem to have key responsibilities for enlightening students about such problematic power relations and preparing them for critical and proactive citizenship. Indeed, results of facilitated action research involving a secondary school science teacher reported here suggest — based on constructivist grounded theory analyses of qualitative data — that teenagers can, after direct instruction and personalized application activities, accommodate often hard-to-discover STS concepts like actor-network theory, dispositifs, semiotics, regulatory regimes, inscriptional (as conscriptional) devices, governmentality, sociotechnical imaginaries and more to analyze 'existing' and envisage future network relations that collectively support their ideological priorities regarding apparently-problematic relationships among fields of science and technology and societies and environments.

Tissue Pedagogies: Engaging with the Commodified State of the Body in Science Education *Matthew Weinstein, Univ. Of Washington-Tacoma*

This paper theorizes a curriculum-pedagogy of tissue economies as a means of engaging capitalist science. It shares my experiences enacting this pedagogy in a science teacher preparation program. Through Waldby, Cooper, et al.'s (Cooper & Waldby, 2014; Waldby & Mitchell, 2006) work on neoliberal regimes of human subjection and journalistic work by Alan MacCleod (2019) documenting how blood and plasma have become major U.S. exports, as well as ethnographic engagements with blood and its material and symbolic productions (e.g., Copeman, 2009), I synthesize a vision of science education (SE) that places the commodification of the body at the center of the curriculum. I discuss how this evolved from earlier work making (human) subjection a focus of SE, which I dubbed Guinea Pig Pedagogy (2004), that foregrounded the relational aspects of science—specifically between the knower and object of science. I discuss how such curricula challenge common and technoutopian framings of STEM education. I describe my use of Rebecca Skloot's (2010) parallel histories of HeLa cells and the Lacks family from whom those cells were stolen and MacCleod's article to guide my students' engagement with the racial and financial economies of science. It also recounts my surprise when I discovered how many of my students were participants in blood/plasma donations for money and explores the complexity of engaging with the-state-of-the-world in education. My conclusion discusses how such tissue pedagogies point to the need to find new purposes beyond those promoted in current policy for SE.

Session Organizer:

John Lawrence Bencze, Ontario Institute for Studies in Education, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Lyn Carter, Australian Catholic University, Melbourne, VIC, Australia

146. Realities Not So Virtual: Application and Concerns about Virtual Reality Technology and Robots

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Inspired by the cinema industry and science-fiction writers, Virtual Reality (VR) and robots have been developing since the 1960s in several domains such as army, education, sexuality and are now largely used in medicine,

from advanced surgery to mental healthcare. Depending on their applications these tools come in many forms. VR technology is typically a helmet allowing visual access to a virtual environment, and equipped with captors to replicate instantaneously the movements of the body and increase physical sensations. Robots can be more or less humanised in their functions and outlook. These tools can be used to play, replay or anticipate social situations. But their development raises numerous social, ethical, and ontological issues. Among them: What does the hybrid status of reality conveyed by these tools do to the conception of the situations in which they are implemented? In what ways do they impact the social, personal and professional worlds in which they are introduced? How does VR and robots convey hopes and challenges specific to each context? How do these tools and the scenarios they support reproduce social scripts as well as unequal categories and worldviews? This panel aims to gather research that tackles these non-exhaustive questions, in order to understand the forms and consequences of the development of virtual reality technologies and robots in various contexts.

Participants:

Touch, Engineered: Haptic Interfaces in Virtual and Augmented Reality *Valentina Turrini, Università Cattolica del Sacro Cuore*

Visionary engineers, driven by the realization that touch is at the core of the way we interact with our surroundings, are experimenting with innovative interfaces which provide tactile feedback, aiming to fulfill fantasies of bodily immersion in virtual environments. Second-generation VR and AR have indeed prompted new flows of capital into research on digitized touch, so that we seem to find ourselves in the midst of a technological 'haptic moment' (Parisi, Paterson, & Archer, 2017). Haptic devices are starting to be tested in various contexts such as tele-robotics, remote surgery, manufacturing, military training, videogames, mobile communication, and arts. These technologies are even creating the opportunity - for the first time in human history - to locate and control a virtual counterpart of our own body in places far from the actual position where it happens to be. Haptic interfaces are indeed often connected to visions of technology as a means to 'augment' the bodily competences, the perceptions, and ultimately the boundaries of human condition. Using a Social Construction of Technology (SCOT) inspired approach (Pinch and Bijker, 1984), the investigation consisted in collecting qualitative data through interviews and ethnography at international conferences and in laboratories where knowledge about digitized touch is collectively created and shared. The different meanings or potentialities of use which respondents attributed to haptic technologies have been analyzed; these meanings are linked to different visions about the practices that could benefit from the implementation of these novelties, and to wider social discourses regarding technological innovation.

AI and Sex Robots: An Examination of the History and Technologization of Sexuality *Keif Godbout-Kinney, Memorial University of Newfoundland*

The emergence of sex robots with rudimentary but slowly advancing AI is a relatively new phenomenon, and there is little understanding about what the possible implications of these automatons could be, particularly regarding their impact on human sexuality. However, there is a historical fascination with automata that can be traced to policies in WWII, colonial voyages from the French and Spanish, and the ancient Greeks (Ferguson, 2010). Drawing on a number of historical and media sources, this paper looks at modern AI and sex robots, specifically how they function as a means by which a certain kind of sexuality is constructed and maintained. Beginning with an examination of the past, I look at this relationship of sexuality and technology and the ways it has shaped not only how each of these categories are viewed in relation to each other, but also the ways that they have had a direct impact on the development of social practices. Specifically, I am interested in the ways sex

robots could be used to reinforce harmful gender stereotypes about women, and lead to sexual violence. Because they are such a new phenomenon, relatively little has been written about sex robots, although there is increasing speculation amongst technology scholars that they could have detrimental effects on human interpersonal relations. This project aims to fill this gap in the literature around the topic of sex robots, with the approach being theoretical and drawing on historical sources to learn from what came before.

Cyber Toy Stories - (Re)scripting Technosexual Utopias in Marketing Teledildonics *Ekaterina Osipova, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies; Azadeh Badieijaryani, TU Wien; Katta Spiel, TU Wien*

Remote-controlled sex toys, or teledildonics, affect multiple realities of intimacies, relationships and identities, among them notions of gender and sexuality – leading to larger ramifications regarding the social discourses and practices of how these are negotiated. We use ontological politics (Mol, 1999; 2002) to understand how the sex tech company Kiiroo acts in this space. Additionally, we delve into technosexual scripts (Waidzunus & Epstein, 2015) inscribed into Kiiroo’s products and advertising thereof. Employing feminist critical discourse analysis, we analyze various blog posts, commercials, and talks, and conduct a material exploration of the company’s products, app, and collaborating virtual reality porn sites. Our research shows that by portraying a technologized utopia, Kiiroo presents its technology as an innovative and avant-garde local and global good – both optimizing sexual relationships, and improving the health and safety of their customers. While teledildonics have a potential of queering and crippling sexual interactions and, thus, fostering empowerment and inclusivity, Kiiroo’s enactments and inscriptions of the technology (re)enforce cis-hetero-normative concepts of sex, intimacy, and relationships, including the coital imperative. Thereby a range of identities and practices are marginalised, ignored and effectively excluded. Contrary to the company’s promises, we show how such enactments potentially result in a dystopia characterized by security nightmares around intimacies and dire consequences for mental and physical health, safety, and consensual sexual interactions. We close on a range of recommendations for designers to consider and account for the perils of intimacy in the space of sex toys more explicitly.

Session Organizers:

FORNER Elsa, 1983

Marie Le Clainche Piel, CNRS - Centre d'Etude des Mouvements Sociaux

147. Science and Technology Studies Journal editors' meeting

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

The editorial board meeting of Science and Technology Studies, the house journal of European Association for the Social Study of Science and Technology.

Session Organizer:

Salla Sariola, University of Helsinki

Chair:

Heta Tarkkala, University of Eastern Finland

148. Alternative Practices for RRI in the UK and Japan

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Best practices are an appealing idea—we all want what’s best—but they can come with unintended consequences. By assuming that what has worked well in one context should work well in another, best practices can erase difference when exported from one place to another. In this session we are interested in how we might develop alternative practices for responsible research and innovation (RRI) in the UK and Japan, learning from each other while remaining sensitive to context. In the UK, RRI has been presented as a way of opening up conversations about the goals and

shape of science and technology, but is increasingly being interpreted as as a narrowly framed set of issues to be checked off a list. Meanwhile, Japanese academics and policy makers are actively developing approaches to RRI and looking to Western contexts with more established programmes for models to adopt, thereby risking not only reproducing limited framings but also eliding contextual particularities. Here, we draw on our experiences in each country to generate ways of identifying, discussing and propagating “alternative practices” for RRI. Our cases span synthetic biology, molecular robotics, artificial intelligence, and molecular medicine. We aim to increase the visibility of RRI as an active and unsettled area of concern in need of continued reflection and elaboration, and to refresh the RRI conversation in light of tendencies to reduce RRI to narrowly framed institutional requirements.

Participants:

Histories of “responsibility” in Japan and the UK *Yuko*

Fujigaki, University of Tokyo; Robert David Jonathan Smith, University of Edinburgh; Steve Sturdy; Ryuma Shineha, Osaka University

We historicize the idea of “responsibility” in relation to science and technology. By charting the multiple and contested notions of responsibility that scientists have espoused from the early twentieth century to the present, we illuminate the very specific and contingent understanding of “responsibility” embodied in RRI. Scientists have used the word “responsibility” strategically, at different times and in different contexts – including the Pugwash conferences from the 1950s, and the rise of the new left in the 1970s – to project their preferred views of how science should relate to wider society. Comparing the Japan and the UK highlights both the context-specific meanings that scientists have associated with responsibility, and the way that those specific meanings have come into conversation with one another. Notably, Japanese physicists played a major role in defining scientific responsibility in the years after the second world war, not just in Japan but internationally, in their capacity as representatives of the only country to have experienced nuclear bombing. In thinking about the purpose and desirability of alternative practices for RRI, it is helpful to consider the professional and wider societal aims and implications of existing configurations and construals of “responsible” research and innovation – including how those configurations may shield scientists from certain kinds of responsibility while embracing others. Showing how the idea of “responsibility” has been deployed in the past provides a means of historicizing, relativizing and thereby evaluating how current claims to scientific responsibility may be configured in different contexts.

Configurations of Public Engagement, Science Policy, and Science Communication: Who is Responsible, and for What?

Jusaku Minari, Kyoto University; Niki Vermeulen, University of Edinburgh; Erika Amethyst Szymanski, Colorado State University; Koichi Mikami, Keio University; Robert David Jonathan Smith, University of Edinburgh

We juxtapose major historical developments in science communication and public engagement in Japan and the UK, toward demonstrating differences in not only how the “public” is defined but also why its presence is considered important. Many stories have been told about the trajectory of how science communication and public engagement policy have developed in the UK, the EU, the US, and Australia, where largely comparable events have unfolded. In contrast, the Japanese government’s recent experiences are much less well known internationally, and do not follow the same pattern of intellectual movements. We highlight these contrasts to challenge and open up dominant Western narratives, toward making more space for considering how discussions on science communication and public engagement have evolved in different ways in diverse settings. Simultaneously, we point to idiosyncrasies in the UK experience that may not always be observed as such. In so doing, we demonstrate that connections—or, as it may be, the absence of

connections—between RRI and science communication and public engagement cannot be taken for granted and must be addressed in specific contexts.

Teaching Responsibility in/and Responsible Teaching *Koichi Mikami, Keio University; Pablo Schyfter, Science, Technology and Innovation Studies, The University of Edinburgh; Ryuma Shineha, Osaka University; Robert David Jonathan Smith, University of Edinburgh; Yuko Fujigaki, University of Tokyo*

STS has developed useful methods for teaching how science and technology shape and are shaped by historical, social, and cultural phenomena. However, STS scholars in both Japan and the UK are now also tasked with teaching Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) and training future scientists to be responsible scientists. In this presentation, we consider how conventional STS pedagogy can be adapted to satisfy this new expectation. Specifically, we reflect on the role of the case study, a stalwart standby in many forms of STS teaching. By comparing and contrasting our teaching experiences in Japan and the UK, we reflect productively on our teaching practices and how case studies can contribute to them. For instance, case studies can give substance to otherwise abstract concepts like ‘responsibility.’ We introduce and examine the notion of ‘proximity’ in order to consider how relevant and comprehensible case studies are to students’ lives, training and future work. We can select and design empirical examples to increase proximity and so use case studies to foster student engagement and reflection toward increased critical capacity. Based on our teaching experiences and our reflections, we present different forms of case studies: disasters, successes, controversies and imaginary futures. We use those to consider how STS can orient and configure its pedagogy in order to teach responsibility responsibly.

Responsible Research and Innovation as Long-Term

Collaboration: STS Involvement in Artificial Intelligence in Japan and Synthetic Biology in the UK *Jane Calvert, Edinburgh University; Arisa Ema*

Collaborations between social scientists and humanities scholars and scientists and engineers are central to many activities described as responsible research and innovation (RRI). This presentation compares and contrasts our experiences of STS involvement in artificial intelligence in Japan and synthetic biology in the UK. We show that although we work in two different technoscientific fields in two different countries, there are many similarities between our experiences. There is a difference, however, in our relationships to “ethical, legal and social issues” or ELSI research, which has proven productive in STS research on AI in Japan, but can be a constraint when studying synthetic biology in the UK. Drawing from our work in both these fields, the presentation argues for the value of long term, incremental collaborations, built up organically and informally over time. These types of collaboration ideally result in a form of responsibility that is distributed amongst disciplines, rather than delegated to the STS researcher, and they provide an example of “alternative practices” for RRI.

The Soba Restaurant and the Oyster Bar: Peripheral Spaces for Responsible Research and Innovation *Erika Amethyst Szymanski, Colorado State University; Ryuma Shineha, Osaka University; Ken Kawamura; Niki Vermeulen, University of Edinburgh; Jane Calvert, Edinburgh University; Robert David Jonathan Smith, University of Edinburgh*

As STS researchers working closely with scientists and engineers, we have been invited into, created, reluctantly entered, and stumbled upon many different kinds of spaces, some of which might be considered spaces for responsible research and innovation. We discuss a selection of these spaces, drawing on our work in synthetic biology in the UK and molecular robotics

in Japan. These include a multidisciplinary workshop, a policy meeting, an art performance, a public engagement event, and several panels at scientific conferences on the ethical, legal and social issues raised by our fields of study. Many of these spaces were owned and controlled by scientists and engineers, and our participation in them was constrained by pre-existing frames. But even in those spaces we designed ourselves it was difficult to challenge institutionalized practices and dominant understandings of the relationship between the natural and social sciences. We often found that those places that were most conducive to provocative, productive and critical cross-disciplinary dialogue were at the peripheries of formal events. We explore the importance of peripheral spaces for RRI, drawing on the examples of interactions that took place at a soba restaurant and an oyster bar.

Session Organizers:

*Erika Amethyst Szymanski, Colorado State University
Koichi Mikami, Keio University*

149. Querying Algorithms and Digitization from Cybernetics to Surveillance

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This panel assembles diverse scholarship critically investigates the practices of digitization and algorithms. Stretching from the recent events such as the Cambridge Analytica scandal to the history of the history of Project Cybersyn in Chile, to the use of zoom in university classrooms in Brazil, this panel reflects on into the relational details of digital and computational technologies.

Participants:

How the Algorithmic Turn of Prediction Transforms Privacy
Carsten Martin Ochs, University of Kassel

While the distinction private/public is central for modern societies, its status is oftentimes problematized in discussions around digitization and algorithms. However, as any closer look at the controversies turning around ‘digital privacy’ quickly reveals, the societal-structural role and meaning of privacy is not quite clear in most accounts of the problematic. In my talk I will present the main insights of my habilitation thesis submitted in January 2021: a socio-technical history reconstruction of privacy that conceptualizes the latter as an instrument allowing individuals to deal with structural contradictions arising for individual self-constitution since the 18th century. This way, I will identify four types of informational privacy that have emerged in the course of history for structural reasons: reputation management, the dominant technique of the 18th century; retreat, the chief privacy technique of the bourgeois society of the 19th century; information control, the dominant technique of 20th century’s organized modernity (Wagner); and blurring, the technique suited to the contemporary constellation. Having done so, I will focus on the present, thus demonstrating how contemporary self-constitution is restrained in the structural contradiction between data-based visibility to increase individual options for action on the one hand (‘digital optionality’, e.g. Castells 1996), and data-based predictivity to decrease options for action on the other hand (‘digital predictivity’, e.g. Zuboff 2019). The algorithmic turn to prediction thus profoundly transforms privacy again: it is the openness of future that requires protection in contemporary privacy regimes. (STS) Discussions around algorithms and privacy should take this historical insight into account.

New walls: Interrogating “boulder specs” of the VLE from the ground up *Birgit Ruth Buergi, University of Cambridge*
Fortifying the walls of an already gated and shielded Cambridge College community throws into stark relief the control functions of a virtual classroom used for small-group teaching. Academic institutions swiftly swapped lecture halls and seminar rooms with web-based meeting platforms, (e.g. Zoom), originally designed

and engineered for conference calls and similar socially-distanced gatherings in the corporate world. With ethnographic insights gained from convening a cross-disciplinary research and study skills programme for undergraduate and postgraduate students, I set out to interrogate the inbuilt (default) settings for Zoom meetings. In strictly technical terms, what does “firewalling” and “waiting rooming” do to the learning experience, and the overall student experience during the COVID-19 pandemic that sent university students home. Each click that activates or deactivate barriers between the convenor and the participants is documented and discussed in this brief excursus that leads inside the techno-social infrastructure of this virtual fortress, conceptually framed in terms of ‘splinternets’, though in the singular. Central to this field-based, micro-scale analysis of the interior design of the Zoom meeting room at small-group level is a particularly irritating effect of online teaching and learning. “Zoom Fatigue” (not classified as a syndrome in the Diagnostic and Statistical Manual of Mental Disorders (DSM), yet) has been mobilised as an argument to justify disengagement from co-creational curricular activities in spite, or perhaps because of the heightened level of intimacy and connectedness, networked educational connectivity engenders.

(Re)creating “society in silico”: simulations, digital doubles and behavioural modification in the Cambridge Analytica data scandal *Vito Laterza, University of Agder*

This paper provides a different angle to understand the Cambridge Analytica (CA) data scandal. It focuses on the role of models and simulations in the big data campaigning tools CA allegedly used, and their epistemological and ontological potential to produce and reproduce voters’ digital doubles that would first colonise and eventually replace the analogue selves they were related to. The paper explores CA whistleblower Chris Wylie’s 2019 autobiographical account of CA main actors’ visions of creating “society in silico”, and integrates and revises Zuboff’s surveillance capitalism framework with Debord’s classic theory of the Spectacle. The main argument presented here is that the dystopian simulations played as real life experiments by surveillance capitalist firms such as CA have the ultimate goal of replacing analogue humanity with digital humanity – the two kinds are ontologically different albeit dialectically related. The predictive models that these simulations produce are only as good as the capacity of the digital doubles in the simulations to shape the behaviour of analogue selves in line with the simulations’ parameters and goals.

Stafford Beer and cybernetics in Chile: the state, autonomy and democracy. *Thomas Swann; Juan Felipe Espinosa-Cristia, Universidad Nacional Andrés Bello*

While Stafford Beer’s work is hailed by many as revolutionary, a set of loosely associated critiques identify it – and cybernetics more generally – as a form of functionalism concerned with social engineering by a technocratic elite (Burrell and Morgan, 1979; Ulrich, 1981; Tiqqun, 2010; Firth and Robinson, 2020). This paper addresses these critiques by examining the social and political context of Beer’s work in Chile, drawing on James C. Scott’s articulation of the modern state as an organisational form that ‘undermines individuals’ capacities for autonomous self-governance’ (1998: 349) and creates ‘a terrain and a population with precisely those standardised characteristics that will be easiest to monitor, count, assess, and manage’ (ibid.: 81-2). Suggesting an overlap between Scott’s description of the modern state and the functionalism critique, the paper assesses whether Allende’s regime and Project Cybersyn point towards the kind of modern statecraft Scott highlights. If it does, this suggests that the functionalism critique holds some weight, in so far as Project Cybersyn is the most influential application of Beer’s cybernetics. If it does not, it will provide a refutation of the functionalism critique, showing that cybernetics does not necessarily entail the kind of authoritarianism identified by these critiques and Scott’s account of the modern state. The paper

concludes by suggesting that radical extensions of Beer’s cybernetics – anarchist cybernetics (Swann, 2018; 2020) and the Viable Relational System (Lavanderos, 2020) – show the potential of cybernetics to align with Scott’s account of local autonomy and democracy that he counterposes to the modern state.

Session Organizer:

Vito Laterza, University of Agder

150. Art, Science and Technology Studies - II: Boundaries and Borders in Art and Science

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Chair: Megan Halpern

Participants:

Interleaving Practices And Critical Kits *Ross Dalziel, Lancaster University, UK*

This paper proposes a method of ‘Interleaving’ as an approach to boundary work between art and science. In the author’s art practice, artists work alongside science; they try to do what scientists do, re-empractising. Disciplines are not bridged seamlessly as if epistemologically flat; no impossible consensus or enclosure is arrived at, but potentially antagonistic borders are negotiated. The paper reflects on ‘critical kits’ – intentional boundary objects that we – the author and collaborators – use to package up practices in biomedical science and engineering for non-scientists or scientists-in-the-making. We also bundle up things often excluded – unacknowledged traces, imperialisms and political commitments, model organisms, supply chains, games, feelings, atmospheres. We do this through a practice based Art PhD embedded in maker culture – at a makerspace (Liverpool), a charity for neuromuscular conditions (Cheshire), and in biomedical teaching (Lancaster University), sensitive to bodily histories. These kits are not art objects, they are convivial by-products of interventions, solidarities. It’s an art practice that uses interleaving to do boundary work and unravel its own authority, autonomy and ontologies in favour of a set of commitments to other social worlds. Making kits as participant observers we notice diverse practices – that stick together but stay separate, that interact, but without synthesis – that interleave with each other without erasing difference – like in the multi-species labour of leavening and kneading bread. We think with Interleaving Practices as an interdisciplinary heuristic and generous method for art and science boundary workers in precarious worlds.

Verfremdung and artistic science *Kasper Ostrowski, Aarhus University*

“The natural must be made to look surprising” (Esslin 1961). Artistic science and craft based research blur demarcations between different areas of doings and thinkings. In this presentation I aim to promote the dramaturgic notion ‘Verfremdung’ as part of the repertoire of artistic STS science. Departing from a research project entitled Empirical Prints (EP) I demonstrate how de-familiarizing can be done in practice. EP was initiated as an open-ended experimental project in 2014. The craft based research project combined STS perspectives with on-site printmaking and ran through 2017. EP invited participants (in different ways) to source objects for a mobile printing press and partake in an ethnographic investigation fabricating relief prints. The mobile printing press worked as an inscription device investigating a novel way of collecting empirical materials and re-enact them in an aesthetically surprising and interesting manner. The set-up has – amongst multiple other sites – partaken in ‘Making and Doing’ sessions at former STS conferences. This talk centers on parts of the findings – specifically the relations between the reclaimed objects and the prints. The ethnographic conversion between object, ink, paper and people centers on the act of fabrication and the artistic translation simultaneously blurs

and displays the connection between input and output. Litter and marooned things were turned into objects of inquiry, making us re-consider the naturalness of the natural and exploring the potential otherness in and of the mundane. I argue that *Verfremdung* can expand our methodological vocabulary and aid our understanding of the world we inhabit.

What Kind Of Sound Is A Good Sound -- The Auditory Aesthetics Constructed By Sound Technology *Qiushi Xu, Southern University of Science and Technology (SUSTech)*

Is there an objective standard for what is a good sound? If so, what is that standard? How is it formed? If not, what are the criteria on sound awards such as Grammy? Nowadays, with highly developed sound technology, people are exposed to plenty of sound products produced by recording technology in their daily life. Taking the sound of piano as an example, this research explores how sound technology shapes the criteria of what a good sound is and constructs the auditory aesthetics. On the basis of empirical research, this research conducted a one-year fieldwork inside recording studios and concert halls in Cornell University and Ithaca College to investigate the social producing process of piano sound, and conducted qualitative interviews with pianists and sound engineers to investigate the invisible technical power. Specifically, this research represents two cases: one is simulating the flawed technology -- the criteria of sound that are disciplined by recording technology, and the other is faking perfection -- the public and the pianist that are disciplined by sound technology. From these two cases, this research reveals the construction of sound technology in sound art and auditory aesthetics. Sound technology disciplines sound engineer, pianist and composer, and reshapes the auditory aesthetics of public; consequently, it changes the piano art. This research delves into the entanglement and interaction between sound art, sound technology and society.

Boundariness: Developing Boundary Objects, Agents, Processes and Practices of Transdisciplinary Collaboration in Artistic Research *Alexandra R. Toland, Bauhaus Universität Weimar*

The use of boundary objects in making and thinking about art is relatively new. Recent publications by Johanna Schindler (2018), who takes an inductive approach to identifying boundary objects in artistic research, Ruth Benschop (2009) and Dehlia Hannah (2013), who both look at the value of STS in art critique, as well as the „Boundary Objects“ exhibition, curated by Sophie Goltz at Kunsthaus Dresden (2015), provide insight for developing Star and Griesemer’s (1989) pioneering work on boundary objects through artistic practice. For artists, the “objectness” of Star and Griesemer’s approach can provide a flexible, tangible, and highly affective instrument for collaboration that differs from other forms of objects, such as e.g. Hans-Jörg Rheinberger’s idea of epistemic objects, Bruno Latour’s idea of hybrid objects, Timothy Morton’s idea of hyperobjects, or Jocelyn Scheirer and Rosalind Picard’s use of affective objects. The pragmatism of boundary objects allows artists to contribute to multilateral knowledge transfer processes without diminishing their claims to epistemological autonomy or creative novelty. At the same time, the “boundariness” of Star and Griesemer’s approach allows for new interpretations, inviting models of boundary agents, boundary processes, and boundary practices to emerge. For interdisciplinary research and teaching, especially in institutional contexts of third-party funding, network building or curriculum development, boundary objects can be a powerful tool for establishing common goals, sharing methodologies, and communicating results. This paper presents several case studies that examine the use of boundary objects and their derivative conceptualizations in inter- and transdisciplinary research settings including artists.

Session Organizer:

Hannah Star Rogers, Science, Technology and Innovation

Studies, The University of Edinburgh

151. Borderlands and/as Machine: Technoscience in Unequal and Uncertain Lifeworlds II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Machines are central artifacts in the study of science and technology. As both the products and producers of ways of being, machines play an important role in the making and unmaking of lifeworlds. The development of converging technologies that make computing power possible is often described in frontier language. Silicon Valley and its network of engineers, technicians, and companies take on the roles of pioneers demarcating new territory for others to inhabit. This territory is positioned as a zone of encounters between various forces, a space from where human ingenuity takes flight and that is slowly populated by natives who produce new ways of thinking and of being. The language of frontiers, pioneers, and natives in technoscience brings into the fold consideration of imperial formations, that is practices, concepts, and bodies that articulate equivocal rules and areas of belonging and exclusion. This panel brings together concepts and ways of tracing relations from the fields of Feminist STS, Latina/o Studies, and Critical Ethnic Studies to think about the practices of technoscience in the making of unequal and uncertain worlds. We invite papers dealing with a range of actors and actants within and beyond the United States. Possible topics and approaches include: - Comparative racial formations and technical infrastructures - Black, Indigenous, and People of Color (BIPOC) as critical actors in technoscience - Technoscience in the Borderlands - Concepts emerging from “border thinkers” as ways to bridge social and technical domains - Borderlands theory as a way to rethink STS

Participants:

Bordering Study *Teresa Naval, UCSD*

This paper looks at the “student” as a legal and bureaucratic formation created and maintained through the university and the nation-state, particularly through the management of artifactual borders like visas. I look at how these processes have been managed in the University of California system in three different historical moments when there were moments of rupture in the settling of the “student” as a legal category: in the 1880s, post World War II, and in the 2000s. By examining these moments, I trace how visas that involve training (either “studying” on an F1 or J1 or “working” on an H1B, and the (dis)continuities among them) have been regulated in university policy and in immigration law. I explore how the flow and containment of these artifactual borders highlight contradictions between the public university system and the private interests that sustain. Finally, I conclude by reflecting on the relationship between the figures of the “citizen-worker” and the foreign national and how it sustains and informs contemporary U.S. hegemony and the internationalization of higher education.

“Blocked” Identities: Biometric Frontiers from Tribal to Urban Pakistan *Zehra Hashmi, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor*

The movement of ethnic Pashtuns, migrating from tribal areas bordering Afghanistan to other parts of Pakistan, is contingent on biometric-based identity cards that authenticate Pashtuns as citizens. Yet, these Pashtun migrants’ spatial histories—complicated by a proximity to the Afghan border, trans-national family networks and multiple migration pit-stops—prevent them from presenting neat, verifiable forms of identification. These complications manifest themselves in “blocked” identity cards: the majority of migrants in one Pashtun neighborhood in Islamabad, Tamol, have identity cards that have been placed under “citizenship verification” by the National Database and Registration Authority (NADRA). This paper explores migrants’ collective understanding of how and why a socio-technical bureaucracy such as NADRA would “block” them. In other words, why does the state identify them to then put this recognition in question? This paper delves into how Pashtun migrants theorize blockages within this information infrastructure (Bowker and Star 1999, Edwards 2003, Fisch

2018). It foregrounds how these theories are spatialized and connected to forms of bordered belonging and experiences of multiple displacements. Exploring the friction between migrant experiences and NADRA's identification practices, this paper situates the neighbourhood of Tarnol within the securitized, planned capital city (Feldman 2015). It then examines how a biometric system (Rao 2013, Cohen 2019), enabled by databased functions (Franklin, Halvey and Maier 2005), expands its space-making qualities to conjure internal borders (Alimia 2019) and ultimately produce a techno-frontier (Tsing 2015). This paper centers how Pashtun migrants navigate life in interconnected borderlands as they build strategies for accessing an identity database.

Escape Maps: Satellite Navigation and Migrant Mobility along the French-Italian Border *Celine Eschenbrenner*

This paper explores the role satellite navigation systems play in the experience of migrants crossing the border from Italy to France. The French-Italian border unfolds over twelve miles of mountain land and rises 8,000 feet high on average. It is patrolled by hundreds of soldiers equipped with thermic binoculars, high-sensitivity microphones, and snowmobiles, whose job it is to intercept migrants along cross-border trails to send them back to Italy. Drawing from two months of fieldwork in a refuge administered by no-border activists in an Italian border town, I show how migrants collaborate with activists to dissolve the border's capacity to regulate movement through navigation technologies. Every week, activists embark on strenuous pathfinding expeditions along cross-border trails all the way to France, during which they paint trees and rocks with arrows, and record the coordinates of their marks in their phones. They pin down the locations of soldiers when they meet them. Using smartphone-based navigation applications such as maps.me, activists are able to share their escape routes with the migrants who stop by the refuge before they attempt to cross the border. This paper brings together questions of mobility, navigation, activism, and surveillance. It contributes to STS and migration studies by attending to the forms of knowledge which are forged and endure in the gaps of surveillance, and which deflate the border's ability to affect people's lives.

Undocumented: Biometric Histories, Administrative Malfeasance, and Medical Abuse in ICE Detention Centers *Diana Flores Ruiz, UC Berkeley*

The more biometric data, global bordering logics go, the better. In this paper, I examine a context in which border agents strategically limit the production and circulation of biometric data: medical abuse in ICE detention centers. I trace a working history of contracted software platforms, clerical practices, and reports of system failures in immigrant detention medical record keeping. I argue that the process of digitizing medical records facilitates medical abuse in ICE detention centers. Customs and Border Patrol and ICE use different record management systems that do not communicate or sync with one another, leaving an administrative gap of manually entering vital health information into detention center software platforms. ICE staff members have mangled vital data input. Various software platforms have failed to notify, sync, or update information for medical workers. If a detainee is transferred, their medical information is not guaranteed to follow. From these 'gaps' and 'glitches' in the system emerge forced sterilization, sexual abuse coverups, severe mental distress (including death by suicide), and a plethora of other preventable harms. Rather than a clean and swift automated transition from paper to PDF, the process of digitizing records and adapting electronic notation practices creates the conditions for erasure, omission, and obfuscation in patient care and patient harm. These acts of administrative malfeasance have lethal or permanently life-altering consequences for detained immigrants. I focus on the mechanics of digital medical record management through the lens of administrative violence in order to account for the border machine's everyday production of unequal worlds.

Session Organizers:

Hector Beltran

Iván Chaar López, The University of Texas at Austin

Chair:

Hector Beltran

Discussant:

Iván Chaar López, The University of Texas at Austin

152. The Subjects and Objects of Interface, from AI to Robotics: Postphenomenological Studies

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

When thinking about questions of human-technology relations, it quickly becomes clear that there are no rigid distinctions between where the human user begins and our artifacts end. And these distinctions are only becoming further blurred by advancing robotics, AI, and predicative algorithms. The postphenomenological perspective has proven useful for addressing these kinds of issues of interface, and for helping to conceive of the co-constitution of humans and their technologies. Cathrine Hasse begins our panel with her anthropological studies of human learning and attention, exploring the kinds of futures that people imagine with robotics. Daniel Susser continues with a paper that explores the implications of the incessant work of predictive algorithms upon us for our status as human subjects. In our third paper in this session, Fernando Secomandi uses postphenomenological ideas to draw out biases built into AI and algorithms, exploring how this occurs at the level of interface. Next Stacey Irwin reflects on how subjects are constituted through the mediation of social media. And Richard S. Lewis reviews his posthuman methodology, which combines postphenomenological and other insights for approaching issues of interface in new ways.

Participants:

Imagining Good Relations with Robots? *Cathrine Hasse, Aalborg/Aarhus University*

"How should we live?" Tim Ingold asks in a book on anthropology (Ingold 2018). To answer this question we need to scrutinize diversity in how we imagine the good life with or without robots. Anthropology has made many studies over the years confirming that what is considered good life can differ tremendously. Today some people imagine a good life with robots in the future – whereas others have completely different visions. In a postphenomenological perspective, we can explore variations in relations between humans, technologies and the world, but what about imagined futures with technologies? Learning play a significant role in answering this question. Learning is a fundamental process behind how we pay attention to the world (Hasse 2020) and crucial for future-making (Ingold 2020). There is very likely diversity in material-conceptual learning, which create multistable relations to technology and images (e.g. Rosenberger 2016) and how we pay attention to and with technologies. Good relations is about paying attention and attention is not focusing on a cognitive comprehension single objects singled out from a background (Wellner 2014) but a whole-body process of new learning with preceding learning. Preceding learning as potentials reside not in the head and not even in the body of an individual person but in the relations between a collectivity of persons and their material environment. In this talk, I explore how we as collectives learn to pay attention to materials, non-humans and each other.

Subjects and Objects of Prediction *Daniel Susser, Penn State University*

That we are objects of prediction is an increasingly mainstream concern. As individual and population-level data proliferates, data collectors are able to conduct more and more sophisticated forms of data analysis, giving rise to predictions about everything from a person's creditworthiness to the healthcare costs they are likely to incur, from their odds of success in college to the likelihood they will commit a crime. Data is also used to predict

what people want. Targeted advertising systems attempt to predict people's preferences and desires in order to tailor marketing appeals. Recommender systems use such predictions to personalize people's digital environments, surfacing content, products, and services geared toward their individual tastes and interests. At a more granular level, machine learning and artificial intelligence tools promise to predict—and to influence—individual behavior. And if prediction is a precursor to control, there is reason to worry about what Shoshana Zuboff calls the “instrumentarian power” these technologies of “behavior modification” enable. Amazon has the products we want. Google will find the information we need. Facebook will engage us. Though this sounds nice, stated in the abstract, it is antithetical to practical reason: if our desires are satisfied no matter what we do we needn't try other things, or—importantly—to ask if they are good desires in the first place.

Fair interfaces for AI *Fernando Secomandi, Delft University of Technology*

A growing part of the world population currently relies on AI-enabled products and services on a daily basis, whether in the form of intelligent virtual assistants, recommendation engines, etc. Such applications of AI are often biased, leading to experiences of discrimination, unfairness, racism, among others. Current discussions have tended to locate the source of AI bias on algorithms/datasets, organizations, and societies. In this presentation, I will review these arguments and advance a postphenomenological perspective that takes account of how AI bias is experienced at the interface between humans and AI technologies. Next, I will build on the notions of mediated morality (Verbeek, 2011) and subjectification (Dorrestijn, 2012) to better orient the design of fair AI interfaces.

A Posthuman Method for Situating Technological Relations: A Usability Study *Richard S. Lewis, Prescott College*

We exist within a complex ecosystem of relations with other humans, with other species, with the space we inhabit, with our own past and future experiences, with technologies, and with our mind and body. In order to critically evaluate these relations and interrelations effectively, we need to have an adequate awareness of the complex context that they all exist within. To accomplish this, the researcher has developed a posthuman method that is comprised of a general framework and a specific instrument in order to investigate and analyze how a seemingly singular engagement with a specific technology is, in fact, complexly interrelated. This method leverages the embodied relation as used in postphenomenology and leverages it in order to understand the effects of other groups of relations. This presentation describes not only the posthuman method but a case study of university students and their experience using the method. The students used a new posthuman method in order to situate a specific relation with an innovative technology in order to become more aware of the complexity of interrelations involved, thus becoming better able to critically evaluate their engagement with and the effects of the technology.

Technological Mediation: Reflecting on the Social Media Use Case *Stacey O Irwin, Stacey Irwin*

As the pandemic moved people inside, to physically and social distance from one another, the social side of being human, shifted toward engagement through technology like social media. Some researchers share that social media is not social (Majkut 2010, Turkle 2012). Others look at the current experiences and feel that indeed, social media type environments create and maintain social experiences and connections (Manovich, 2001). Still others see the environment as a central part of media, and social media as a part of that environment (McLuhan, 2005). This paper explores the co-shaping and co-constitution of human-technology-world connections through the lens of social media, to consider and uncover different practices and methods of experiencing our increasingly global and uncertain world

(Verbeek, 2006, Ihde, 1993). Ideas in relation making, modes of knowing, and the circulation of knowledge are considered.

Session Organizer:

Robert Rosenberger, Georgia Institute of Technology

153. Beyond Quackery: Medical Misinformation and the Internet

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

This panel brings together researchers from Harvard, University of California - Los Angeles, University of Michigan, University of Washington, and Penn State to discuss how medical misinformation travels and is quickly amplified through the internet. The panelists will cover methodologies used to research discrete medical misinformation campaigns -- as well as the social movements that spread them. After an introduction on researching medical misinformation, each panelist will present on their own papers. Medical misinformation campaigns have been used over decades and across health issues. In order to illustrate the range in time, tactics, and topics, we will present cases on the anti-vaccination movement, the origins of a COVID-19 rumor, and the false link between abortion and breast cancer. Each case is a lesson in both the strategies employed by the campaign and the methods used by researchers to study it. The panel will cover insights gleaned from agnotology to argue that we are witnessing the emergence of a “mediatic hyper-science” -- where the aim of science deniers is to look more scientific, thoughtful, and responsible than the scientists themselves. Finally, the panel will offer standardized language and frameworks for identifying medical misinformation and media manipulation campaigns; a toolkit for identifying, documenting and mitigating medical misinformation; and tips for academics on talking to and/or working with journalists who cover medical misinformation.

Participants:

Cloaked Science: The Yan Reports *Joan Donovan, Harvard Kennedy School; Jen Nilsen, Harvard University*

We will discuss the process of researching and writing Cloaked Science: The Yan Reports alongside Craig Timberg, a Washington Post reporter who covered the story simultaneously. We will go into the details of researching independently, sharing information and sources, and syncing publishing academic work with journalism. The Yan Report is a misleading article masquerading as science, which falsely claims that the novel coronavirus was made in a Chinese lab. On April 28, 2020, Dr. Li-Meng Yan, a researcher at the University of Hong Kong, fled to the US with support from Steve Bannon and Guo Wengui. They used Yan's story — that she was a whistleblower — to exploit the contentious wedge issue of the unknown origin of COVID-19. This disinformation campaign planted misleading evidence into the scientific literature, muddying the waters about COVID-19 and providing the veneer of scientific legitimacy for the political claim that coronavirus was a Chinese bioweapon. The Yan Report was amplified through right-wing media networks, leading to over a million views on Zenodo, an open-access research data repository. While social media platforms moderated information about the Yan Report after university scientists debunked it, two follow-up Yan Reports were uploaded to Zenodo -- more bluntly pushing the bioweapon narrative while also refuting the academic responses to the original report. Seeding the Yan reports in the scientific community as cloaked science allowed those who linked to them to claim legitimacy while also providing the empirical basis for furthering the political aims of the funders of the reports.

Public Health Misinformation Campaigns *Brian Friedberg, Harvard; Irene Pasquetto, University of Michigan*

Disinformation and media manipulation is a pernicious problem challenging global health and democracy. During the COVID-19 pandemic, media manipulation campaigns dedicated to spreading harmful medical misinformation have flourished online, targeting health experts, undermining legitimate advice, and sowing mistrust and conspiracism. We will address how the public health sector, along with a coalition of civil servants, media workers,

technology companies, and civil society organizations, can identify and respond to the problem of media manipulation, specifically how it spreads medical misinformation online. We will highlight cases of medical misinformation, and provide a framework for public health stakeholders to employ when documenting and responding to media manipulation in their own communities. 1. Establish standardized language and frameworks for identifying medical misinformation and media manipulation campaigns 2. Provide a toolkit for identifying, documenting and mitigating medical misinformation 3. Suggest the establishment of early warning networks across civil society, journalism, and public health institutions We will then introduce Investigative Digital Ethnography and the Media Manipulation Lifecycle model as a means for establishing provenance of disinformation artifacts and process tracing campaigns. To illustrate how the lifecycle model of media manipulation can be used to research and analyze medical disinformation campaigns, we will discuss the ABC Link (Abortion-Breast Cancer Link) campaign and how it is perpetrated in the US by pro-life movements, crisis abortion clinics and “fake” breast cancer research centers. We will show how these actors – working in a networked fashion – utilize the tactic of “cloaked science” as an evangelical tool to popularize and amplify medical disinformation.

The rise of Anti-vaccination activists and influencers in the time of COVID *Kolina Koltai, University of Washington*

Prior to the coronavirus pandemic, the anti-vaccination movement had been flourishing online and has grown dramatically in the past year. The ways the movement has utilized the affordances of social networking and digital platforms laid a solid foundation to capitalize on spreading vaccine misinformation in this time of extended public crisis and uncertainty. In some ways, the events of 2020 and 2021 were the perfect storm for vaccine misinformation to spread and thrive. This session will highlight the ways in which vaccine misinformation and disinformation have continued to spread, despite social networking platforms’ efforts to moderate content. The sessions will discuss the tactics and folk theories that social media users and anti-vaccine activists employ to continue spreading misinformation and promoting vaccine hesitancy. In particular, this session will highlight findings from a research effort titled the Virality Project aimed at conducting real-time rapid response research and analysis on anti-vaccination narratives online. In particular, this project is aimed at following the evolution and spread of vaccine hesitancy narratives and the communities in which they gain traction. In addition, the session discusses how anti-vaccination messaging uses pseudo-scientific language and sources to help promote an image of scientific rigor. The anti-vaccination movement is often characterized as being “anti-science” yet members of these digital communities often exchange a corpus of scientific sources aimed at addressing that criticism. Anti-vaccination content does not fit into an easy dichotomous model of true and false, but rather uses decontextualization techniques and reframing of factual content into a misleading narrative.

Quackery or Science Upside-Down? *Mario Biagioli, University of California - Los Angeles*

Agnology, the study of ignorance, has provided crucial insights in the management of scientific controversies by corporate interests, from the dangers of tobacco smoking to global warming. While framed by an opposition between knowledge and ignorance, light and darkness, the field’s most important contribution has been the thick description of the discursive techniques, business practices, and media tactics aimed at producing doubt, which is exceptionally effective precisely because it is neither truth nor falsehood, neither knowledge nor ignorance. Doubt can make deferring the closure of a controversy look like the scientifically responsible, even moral thing to do – “we ought to pursue more research to properly settle these matters” -- despite the fact that, when mobilized to stall decisions

about global warming, such deferral may have deadly consequences. Through various examples, I argue that rather than the production of ignorance as non-knowledge, we are witnessing the emergence of a “mediatic hyper-science.” The goal is not to directly obfuscate or refute the content of scientific knowledge, but the mimicking of the most distinctive norms of science to make it look like the deniers are more scientific, thoughtful, and responsible than the scientists. These strategies are not aimed at winning “contests of force” (in Latour’s terms), but to find cheap ways (in the literal sense of requiring few resources) to delegitimize the very extensive and expensive science produced by thousands of researchers over decades. Going for a refutation is an expensive, risky business, but doubt is the weapon of the epistemological weak.

Situating Data Curation in the Media Manipulation Life Cycle *Seth Erickson, Penn State University*

Data curation—the work of documenting and improving data to support its value in the long term—is often presented through the lens of the “research life cycle”, as a source of continuity between one research project and another. This paper argues that the research life cycle model of data curation is inadequate for understanding and addressing recent challenges in open science, particularly those associated with the spread of misinformation and coordinated media manipulation. Situating data curation within a “media manipulation life cycle” (Donovan, 2020) clarifies the expanded role research data specialists play in mitigating and responding-to misinformation, and it foregrounds the kinds of expertise and care-work necessary to make open science possible in today’s media landscape. The media manipulation life cycle describes stages of planning, spreading, and responding-to misinformation; the work of data curators pertains at every stage. The paper draws on recent case studies—on “cloaked science” in open science repositories (Nilsen & Donovan, 2021); on the manipulation of open data resources to generate “counter-visualizations” (Lee et al., 2021); and the author’s work on politically-charged attacks of open source COVID modeling research—to illustrate the vulnerabilities of open science practices and points of intersection with curatorial work. Making open science less vulnerable to coordinated misinformation means attending to research data’s circulation and (mis)use beyond the immediate research community, anticipating data’s potential for misuse, and recognizing how tropes of scientific expertise are exploited to spread deliberately misleading information.

Session Organizers:

Jen Nilsen, Harvard University

Joan Donovan, Harvard Kennedy School

Brian Friedberg, Harvard

Irene Pasquetto, University of Michigan

Kolina Koltai, University of Washington

Mario Biagioli, University of California - Los Angeles

Seth Erickson, Penn State University

Discussant:

Christopher Kelty, UCLA

154. **Biotechnologies and Body Interventions: Reorienting Research with Indigenous STS**

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Settler colonialism, its material and epistemological processes and consequences, has been channeled through and determined by notions of the body. The characteristics, capacities, and (dis)similarities ascribed to bodies by disciplinary experts—scientific, medical, and otherwise—has often provided the justification for pathologized, commercialized, and medicalized interventions in human (especially Indigenous) lives and determined the manner in which these interventions would be carried out. It is with this in mind that we in the RELAB and Indigenous STS research lab consider how Indigenous STS, particularly due to its relational

methodological approaches to research, can reframe the ways in which bodies are understood and implicated in a capitalist system that governs bodies through the standardization of health data. In this roundtable, we will consider questions such as: how does Indigenous STS reorient our research of bodies that are co-constituted by disciplinary biotechnologies? How does Indigenous STS inform how we understand bodies and our relations to bodies, land, and health, in our varying technoscientific and biomedical research contexts? Further, how might Indigenous STS function to illuminate the body's place in neoliberal processes, what interventions might Indigenous STS demand in this endeavor, and also, what might this approach obscure? We contend that Indigenous STS produces nuanced and productive understandings of the ways in which the body factors in settler-colonial processes as they exist within, and are extended by technoscientific research and its products.

Presenter:

Wyatt Schiefelbein, University of Alberta, RELAB

Session Organizers:

Hined A Rafeh, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Merissa Daborn, University of Manitoba

Chair:

Jessica Kolopenuk, University of Alberta, RELAB

155. Coastalization: Thinking global relations from the coast - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

Making Models Matter: "Coastalizing" Regional Ocean Modelling in the Netherlands *Jacqueline Ashkin, Center for Science and Technology Studies, Leiden University, the Netherlands; Thomas Franssen, Centre for Science & Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University; Sarah de Rijcke, Centre for Science and Technology Studies (CWTS)*

Studies of climate science show how modeling climate change relies on modeling, knowledge production and infrastructures focused on a global scale (c.f. Edwards 2010). In Dutch ocean modelling, emphasis on the global scale has made way for more regional, coastal, and smaller scale modelling. This is perhaps hardly surprising given that nearly one third of the country sits below sea level, the coast a delicate patchwork of dams and dikes. While global models have resolutions of hundreds by hundreds of kilometers, producing knowledge about the open ocean, models produced by our interlocutors range in resolution from a handful of kilometers all the way down to a few hundred meters, modelling ever closer to the coastline. We ask: how are such small-scale models developed, and what relations – both epistemic and social – are valued through them? Using online semi-structured interviews and digital ethnography, this paper explores scaling in ocean modelling as a valuation practice (c.f. Vatin 2013). Drawing on existing work in science and (e)valuation studies (c.f. Rushforth et. al. 2018), we explore the epistemic choices modelers make within their models (e.g. what types of variables to in/exclude), and their relations with the organization of knowledge production (e.g. knowledge infrastructures, funding). We suggest that while trends in (e)valuation practices and climate change knowledge are oriented towards valuing the global scale, coastalized concerns are reflected in different styles of valuation (c.f. Lee and Helgesson 2019) which in turn make ocean models matter at regional and smaller scales.

MANAGING FISH AND WILDLIFE: Alaska's Resource Management, Political Philosophy, and the Troubles of More-than-Terrestrial Encounters *Andreas Womelsdorf*

Whereas in Plato's *Nómoi*, the polis appears oriented primarily towards the sea (cf., e.g., Elden 2013), late 19th century Heart of Darkness echoes the recalibration of Euro-American political thought and the articulation of settler sovereignty over 'Lands' and 'Waters': Here, the river provides a treacherous connection

between coastal settlement, the hinterland, and, ultimately, the oceanic, colonial Empire (cf., e.g., Benton 2010). Yet, both accounts leave us wondering about the political implications of the foundational distinction between Land and Water, terrestrial and maritime life-worlds. To what extent do contemporary bureaucracies of resource management necessarily imply the distinction between *gaía* and *ōkeanós* (cf., e.g., Bederman 2014); and with what consequences? This paper seeks to address these overarching questions by critically engaging with the structure of Alaska's resource management apparatuses (cf., e.g., Huntington 1992). It will be argued that the distinction between the "Board of Fish" and the "Board of Game", the primary institutions of political decision-making in the state, do not only imply the more fundamental differentiation of terrestrial and maritime eco-systems; more importantly, this organizational feature structurally devaluates the eco-political interconnectedness of Water and Land and is thus incapable of addressing relationships of subsistence based on more-than-terrestrial encounters of Human and Non-Human entities (cf., e.g., Moncrieff & Klein 2003). Thereby, the paper intends to destabilize Latourian notions of 'the Terrestrial' (cf. Latour 2018) eliminating the intricate relations between the emergence of settler colonial, capitalist regimes of domination and configurations of Land and Water (cf., e.g., Povinelli 2018).

Stabilizing State Waters: Emergent Law & Subsiding Land in Coastal Louisiana *Hannah Eisler Burnett, University of Chicago, Department of Anthropology*

As coastlines disappear under rising seas—and as they are bolstered through largescale infrastructural projects—how are property claims adapted, and for whom? In Louisiana, coastal land is disintegrating: since 1932, an area the size of Delaware has vanished from the state's southernmost wetlands. Coastal marshes in Louisiana are 80% privately owned, but when they succumb to open water, ownership over these areas technically reverts to the state. However, access and ownership in these places remains contested—they have been nicknamed "dual-claim land." Uncertainty over these areas has increased alongside plans for coastal restoration projects that will divert large sections of the Mississippi River across eroding marshes, inundating new areas even as they rebuild land in previously submerged places. This paper examines novel legal technologies that seek to cement private and public ownership over emergent nearshore waterways on a rapidly changing coastline. For Louisiana, the stakes of stabilizing state waters are high. Its malleable shoreline has been framed an urgent problem since the 1960s, when Louisiana argued several Supreme Court cases aimed at maintaining claim to offshore oil revenues by fixing the extension of state jurisdiction into the federal territorial sea. I argue that recent innovations in coastal property law are rooted in this history of conflicting sovereignty claims. These legal theories work in tandem with wetland restoration projects and cartographic technologies that aim to make the distinction between land and water legible in a place where these categories have always already been muddy.

The Making and Unmaking of the Coast in

Thiruvananthapuram District: Erosion(s), Accretion(s) and New Development Trajectories *Charles Couvreur, University of Oxford*

Using an assemblage logic, this paper looks at the formation of a frontier—a widely debated term—along the coast of Anchuthengu, home to 'artisanal'-fishers exclusively. It argues that the materiality of the shore, visible to all but underexplored academically, is the backbone of the multi-dimensional coastal transformations generally researched through different angles. This research is empirically grounded around a fishing harbour demanded by the local fishing community ('bottom-up' development), and the permanent, symmetrical geomorphological changes that it induced on the shore, whose

socio-economic consequences it unpacks. North, the traditional shore-fishers reacted to the loss of their shore by adopting ring seine nets, a gear banned in Thiruvananthapuram district. Along with shifting economic and environmental valuations, this triggered a process of differentiation familiar in agrarian contexts but much less in the fisheries. Analytically, this in turn undermines accounts of a relatively stable socio-economic intermediacy notoriously achieved by the artisanal fish-workers in the 1980s and 1990s. Re-appearing and accreting south of the harbour, the shore substantially changes dimensions and meanings to become land. Spending some of its CSR budget on making the harbour safer and improving its image, a major industrial group also encloses the new land to store rocks for the international seaport that they are currently constructing about 40km south. At this juncture, this local assemblage thus folds into a greater, 'top-down' one and rejoins more common patterns of infrastructure development to establish wider coastal frontiers. Through the unmaking and remaking of the coast, a detailed look at the contingent role of nature in processes of accumulation—widely called for in academia—thus unveils chains of multi-dimensional erosions and accretions. Becoming a metaphor for the political ecology of the area, they necessarily also make us reflect on their more fundamental implications for conceptual discussions on the nature-society nexus.

Session Organizer:

Arne Harms, Institute of Anthropology - University of Leipzig

156. Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy/Session 2: Experts and Democracy

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

The Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy (CompCoRe) project, comprising over sixty scholars with interdisciplinary expertise in STS, law, public policy, and the social sciences, has spent a year analyzing national policy responses to the pandemic in sixteen countries across five continents (website: compcore.cornell.edu). Our analysis shows that the pandemic is not simply a public health crisis to be managed by listening to "science" as conventional wisdom would have it. Rather, the Covid-19 crisis is playing out in unexpected and non-linear ways within the interlocking arenas of public health, economy, and politics against a continually shifting terrain of scientific, socioeconomic, and political developments. Our research identifies patterned responses across countries that demonstrate how the pandemic found and exacerbated underlying structural weaknesses in national response systems, and it highlights the need for reforms in current institutional approaches to preparedness in global health crises. Countries represented in CompCoRe include Australia, Austria, Brazil, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, Peru, Singapore, South Korea, Sweden, Taiwan, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The panel will feature comparative analyses of national efforts to enroll reliable epidemiological and biomedical expertise, resolve difficult trade-offs, manage the economic fallout of the pandemic, and build political support for effective implementation, among other topics. We aim to open up new questions about public health sovereignty, crisis management, and global flows of knowledge and power among experts, states, and citizens. You can learn more about CompCoRe at compcore.cornell.edu.

Participants:

Health Democracy in Crisis. Conflicting p\Problematizations of

Democracy and the Covid-19 Pandemic in France. *Brice Laurent, ARMINES; Bastien Lafon, Mines ParisTech*

This paper analyzes current democratic issues related to the public management of the Covid-19 pandemic in France, including the use of legal exceptions and the role of a citizen imagined as a threat to public order and/or a contributor to health policy. We start with the reference to "health democracy" (démocratie sanitaire) in French Covid-related debates. This concept has been used in descriptive and prescriptive ways to characterize an ongoing institutional evolution that seeks to involve patients and other civil society groups in public

expertise. During the crisis, prominent experts identified a failure of health democracy and connected it to shortcomings in public health responses. We build on this critique to explore conflicting problematizations of democracy and the pandemic during the crisis. A first one makes the centralized state the sole actor of the response to a global threat, able to select which democratic norms can be suspended, and in charge of preventing gullible or unruly citizens from threatening social order. A second one gradually made "local adaptation" a central tenet of public health and a condition for the inclusion of citizens characterized by various needs and concerns. Commenting on recent controversial episodes about what can be "adapted" and by whom, we explore the tensions between these approaches. This allows us to read the "failure of health democracy" as the inability to rethink existing political imaginaries about the state and its relationships with its citizens, and as a manifestation of the uncertain nature of the French polity.

Sailing the 'Ship of State' and Safeguarding the Dikes: The Dutch Covid-19 Crisis *Rob Hagendijk, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research, University of Amsterdam*

In today's globalizing world, local history and culture continue to inform Dutch social practices in domains as varied as politics, trade, health care, science, and law. So, we may understand the handling of the Covid-19 pandemic by the Dutch government and population better if we pay attention to that. It also may throw more light on radical critics' protests and their lawsuits against the state in which they argued that measures taken are disproportionate infringements of citizens' rights and freedoms. Disproportionate as the measures were claimed not to be justified by solid scientific evidence. More generally, it might show how considerations of 'proportionality' dominate in Dutch public, professional and stakeholder discourse. And explain how the majority in Dutch 'coalition democracy' seeks to keep the 'Ship of State' and its economy afloat. Don't rock the boat, do urgent repair work, but sail faster to bring us all to the safe harbor of vaccination. The iconic 'Ship of State' offers a promising anchoring point to explore how the Dutch are handling the pandemic. But, equally important may be that other cherished notion referring to water management: 'polder democracy.' Combined these notions tie fate, public trust and engineering at sea as well as behind the dikes, in the past and today.

Brazil's "Vaccine Wars" and the Country's Non-response to Covid-19. *Marko Alves Monteiro, State University of Campinas - UNICAMP; Alberto Urbinatti, University of Campinas; Phillip Macnaghten, Wageningen University; Gabriela Di Giulio, University of São Paulo; Ione Mendes, University of São Paulo; Felipe Reis, University of São Paulo*

This paper offers an initial interpretation of Brazil's chaotic and fragmented response to Covid-19, focusing on the relationship between science/expertise, democracy and public perceptions. We do this through the example of vaccination, analyzing how dramatic failures in the country's efforts to provide mass vaccination reveal important aspects of the country's overall failure to respond to the pandemic effectively. This failure can be broadly interpreted as a broader and longer-term failure of trust in science and the place of expertise in democracy in the country. The paper draws from the authors' participation in the CompCoRe project, involving 59 researchers from 19 countries. We argue that in Brazil, concomitant crises have helped to both erode the capacity of institutions to respond to a public health crisis and erode public trust in publicly produced and available expertise. This relates to ongoing partisan/political disputes involving the Federal government and political/ideological positions aligned with Bolsonaro, a flood of misinformation usually associated with partisan political positions and the way expertise is produced, deployed and disputed by public and state institutions. We conclude that the current context, marked by

deep political polarization, is only understandable if we take into account deep-seated patterns in which science and expertise are organized and deployed. Brazil's state bureaucracy, legitimized to a large degree (especially in health) by technical expertise and by its perceived capacity to deliver "non-political" advice was shook by institutional stresses that show the limitations of this system's legitimacy and ability to function in a context of crisis.

Science, COVID-19 and Dilemmas of the Precautionary Principle. *Sujatha Raman, The Australian National University; Jeremy Baskin, The University of Melbourne; Warren Pearce, iHuman/Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield; John Viana, University of Tasmania*

This paper explores how appeals to precaution and the precautionary principle played out in expert responses to COVID-19 policy matters. Focusing on key examples of expertise that featured in Australia and in the UK, we ask if and how these voices were able to bridge the spheres of science/fact/reason and politics/value/emotion as they sought to address policy. Experts in both countries appealed to precaution as a way of coping with the limitations of scientific evidence, thus complicating broad-brush accounts of whether or not governments were following 'the science'. Precautionary arguments featured in key examples of expert judgment offered in light of incomplete and uncertain science around mask-wearing, travel restrictions, and lockdowns for curtailing disease transmission. In particular, arguments offered by UK experts on mask-wearing resonated with STS work on the need for inclusive understandings of policy expertise that are not wedded to narrow ideas of 'sound science'. However, in the Australian state of Victoria, a 'hard' lockdown that controversially targeted nine public housing towers was critiqued on human rights grounds, but justified in part by the state government on the grounds of the precautionary principle. Legal experts have also drawn on World Health Organization regulations to challenge travel restrictions that are 'not supported by science', again invoking human rights considerations. The use of the precautionary principle vis-à-vis scientific evidence in the context of travel bans and lockdowns thus poses significant dilemmas at the intersection of science and politics which we aim to explore.

Session Organizers:

Sheila Jasanoff, Harvard University

Stephen Hilgartner, Department of Science & Technology Studies/ Cornell University

Ben Hurlbut, Arizona State University

Onur Ozgode, Harvard STS Program, Harvard Kennedy School

Margarita Rayzberg, Cornell University STS

157. Digital (Un)wellness: Power, Health, and Screen Time - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Beyond social media self-control: How to better account for the psychic costs of the attention-economy *Niall Docherty, Microsoft Research New England*

Controversy surrounds the psychological impacts of social media. Some critics argue that platforms' business models, which target user attention for economic gain, are inherently unhealthy for users. Others, such as platforms themselves, claim that negative well-being outcomes arise from 'passive' interactions online, with 'active' use increasing well-being. However, despite ostensibly opposing motivations, both sides of this debate suggest the same curative to social medias' potential harms: individual self-control. Through empirical discursive and material analyses, this paper will show that whether embedded in the self-tracking and time-management prophylactic tools released by platforms, or in the mindful user praxis endorsed by their critics, user well-being is configured as an outcome of

healthy digital choices. This operates as a sociotechnical imaginary (Jasanoff & Kim, 2015) that entrenches a thoroughly neoliberal vision of responsibilized well-being. Here, the structural factors crucial to well-being - sufficient housing, income, and health access, for instance, are ignored, with users instead treated as atomistic agents of self-care. This depoliticises digital (un)wellness while maintaining contemporary processes of neoliberalization. To prise open this foreclosure, this paper will present alternative, relationally situated views of digital well-being able to better examine the contributing structural factors that pressure different users unevenly in different use-contexts. Through this type of comparative analysis, this paper will provide the means for the psychic costs of the attention economy to become more precisely legered, allowing the issue of social media well-being to become something more than is currently imagined: a valid site of progressive political intervention and a new locus for social change.

Girls, Gadgets and Gatekeepers: How Families Police Adolescent Mobile Phone Access In The Name of Wellbeing in Mumbai, India *Isha Bhallamudi, University of California, Irvine*

This paper offers an intersectional, Global South perspective on the ways in which gendered moral panics and discourses around digital wellness combine to create inequalities in adolescents' access to digital technology in India. Using a mixed-methods study of 59 group interviews and 278 surveys with adolescents aged 13-15 in Mumbai, India, this paper provides an intersectional analysis of gendered and classed surveillance experienced by adolescents within the home, and the ways in which this serves to create unequal access to digital technology. The findings show how gender and class together, create varying standards of respectable femininity and class distinction that families cultivate in adolescent girls through constant surveillance, policing and socialization. The mobile phone is seen as both a threat and a necessity to the maintenance of these standards of respectability, resulting in families variously enabling or constraining adolescents' access to mobile phones. The discourses employed by parents to justify this surveillance, policing and socialization invisibilize and hide the primacy of gender and class, but rather invoke pathologized ideas about digital addiction, screen time, academic performance, emotional vulnerability, and online sexual violence. This paper makes 3 important interventions useful to STS literature on this topic: 1) Offering Global South perspectives on surveillance, power and digital wellness discourses, normally saturated with Eurocentric theories and empirics, 2) Applying a feminist and intersectional analysis to these questions, offering interdisciplinary lenses and 3) Extending and focusing the analysis to children, who are often overlooked, and not taken as serious actors in their own right.

Negotiations around Digital Wellbeing in Dutch Networked Families *Anouk Mols, Erasmus University; Jason Pridmore, Erasmus University*

Technologies embedded in everyday family life create endless opportunities but also lead to tensions around power, control, and privacy. For example, even when children are not at home, families can stay in touch via messaging apps. Moreover, parents can use surveillance technologies, such as primary and high school student information systems and location tracking apps, to remain informed about their children's whereabouts. Privacy concerns, (lateral) surveillance practices, and unequal divisions of digital literacy and control affect the digital wellbeing of all family members. Whereas not all families are 'networked' to the same degree, many are facing similar dilemmas around digital practices in relation to digital wellbeing. Therefore, our study explores how families negotiate intrafamilial technology practices. We provide an in-depth account of how six Dutch families use technologies on a daily basis and how they manage tensions around power, control, and privacy. We use qualitative

interviews and a media scroll back activity whereby parents and children between 12-18 share how they use technologies and discuss their personal strategies to manage tensions in their family. Our study highlights negotiations of power around digital parental supervision, expectations in family communication, and privacy concerns. Our findings contribute to literature about technology use, digital literacy, and privacy in family contexts as studied in the fields of human-computer interaction and STS-inspired media studies. Moreover, we foreground sociomaterial relations between family members and technologies in order to provide suggestions for parents/guardians and educators on how to balance autonomy, privacy, and support vis-à-vis digital wellbeing.

Privacy As Digital Wellbeing: The Relationship Between Privacy Practices And Digital Wellbeing During Lockdown
Katja Sara Pape de Neergaard, Katja de Neergaard

The Covid-19 pandemic and subsequent lockdown resulted in an increased digitalization of the home, and thereby presents a unique occasion to examine intimate relationships with digital technologies. This paper explores how such technologies are involved with shaping experiences of privacy, and how this has implications for digital wellbeing. Empirically, the paper is based on interviews and observations conducted during lockdown in Denmark from March to June 2020, with more than 200 participants discussing disturbances and digital reordering of everyday life. The paper shows how digital technologies brought areas of public life far into the home and created new types of digital encounters. Participants' ability to comfortably navigate this depended on individual resources and circumstances, especially in relation to patterns of employment and conditions within the home. The paper finds that digital technologies are deeply involved with producing or breaking down the thresholds of privacy, and that the increased digitalization of the private sphere created new social norms and privacy practices. Here, privacy as self-determination emerged as a crucial aspect of digital wellbeing, as a way of retaining individual autonomy in digital settings. Furthermore, the paper discusses how the combined experience of lockdown and increased digitalization brings attention to digital wellbeing as a complex relationship between digital technologies, the materiality of the home, and the individual experience of being (dis)connected. The paper contributes by considering how digital technologies are involved with producing different thresholds of privacy, and how the individual experience of managing privacy has consequences for digital wellbeing.

Session Organizers:

Laura Calloway, Indiana University
Alex Beattie, Victoria University Wellington
Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley

Discussant:

Jeremy A Greene, Johns Hopkins University

158. Relating with STS from South Asia II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

At the 2020 4S/EASTS conference, the panel "Locating South Asia in Social Studies of Science and Technology" aimed to bring together research on South Asia that are otherwise scattered across different topical 4S panels. By bringing together the research communities of South Asia, it aimed to render visible and consolidate conceptual vocabularies, epistemological, ontological and ethical concerns, and methods involved in researching South Asia. This year's panel is a "bridgework" that draws together the ongoing effort to revisit different pasts of STS in South Asia to intervene in its present and explore possible future avenues for research, collaboration, interdisciplinary and transnational speculations. Papers that explore the following questions are welcome to apply: 1) How does the STS work in South Asia relate with STS areas and theories including Sociology of Scientific Knowledge, Actor-Network Theory, New

Materialisms, Indigenous and Postcolonial Studies? 2) How do such theories when applied to the context of South Asia emerge with unique sensibilities in your research? 3) How can relating STS to anthropological and sociological work on scientific knowledge and technoscientific development in South Asia question "the imperialism of [Global North] categories" in research as an effort towards decolonizing STS? 4) What are the other sciences that are possible in "a world of sciences" and technologies when technoscience is viewed "from below?" (Harding; Wiley) Hence, this panel also aims to investigate the diversity loss in sciences and livelihood losses due to the (de-)legitimizing tactics of modern science. Papers that focus on any STS areas in the context of South Asia including but not limited to technoscientific development of nation states, computational politics, legal, social and environmental justice, public understanding of science, Anthropocene, and postcolonialism may apply. Bibliography Harding, Sandra G. 2008. *Sciences from below: Feminisms, Postcolonialities, and Modernities*. Durham: Duke University Press. Lal, Vinay. 2010. "Thesis Two: Postcolonialism Has Had Nothing to Say about the Imperialism of Categories." Lal Salaam: A Blog by Vinay Lal Reflections on the Culture of Politics & the Politics of Culture. November 30. <https://vinaylal.wordpress.com/2010/11/30/thesis-two-postcolonialism-has-had-nothing-to-say-about-the-imperialism-of-categories/>. Wiley, Angela. 2016. "A World of Materialisms: Postcolonial Feminist Science Studies and the New Natural." *Science, Technology, & Human Values* 41 (6): 991–1014. doi:10.1177/0162243916658707. Contact: s.a.misria@gmail.com, psrigyan@uci.edu Keywords: South Asia, diversity, scientific knowledge, technoscientific development, STS geographies

Participants:

Experience -Based Expertise: A Case Study Of The Proposed Hydro Electric Power Project In Athirappilly
Blesil T K, Central University of Gujarat

Kerala State Electricity Board (KSEB) proposed its 6th dam project on Chalakudy river near the Athirappilly water fall in 1979. This project was opposed by various environmental movements and environmental NGOs in Chalakkudy. They did so due to its hydrological and ecological non feasibility and to protect the Athirappilly waterfall and biodiversity of the inundation area. However, the long-term ecological debates have lasted more than thirty-three years. This paper is based on semi-structured interviews with members of the environmental movements, technical experts, Kadar Adivasis and independent scientists to investigate the context and reasons for the technical debate that emerged from the public. The first part of this paper demystifies the nature of wider public participation and its limitations in the Athirappilly debates with its focus on three stages of the historical development of the environmental movements. The second part of this paper describes the misconceptions of the lay expertise contribution in sociology of scientific knowledge (SSK) and it is replaced with the experience-based expertise for technical debates related to the Athirappilly project. Finally, this paper concludes that the proposed Athirappilly project is not technically viable and this reality was opened up by the experience-based expertise through its long-term engagement with hydrological studies.

Inclusive management of cities through the perspective of Actor-Network Theory
Maitrayee Mullick, IIT Kharagpur; Archana Patnaik, IIT Kharagpur

The urban-centric COVID-19 pandemic amplified the urban challenges of burgeoning population, necessitating the smart and inclusive management of cities. In this context performance of Indian smart cities and their Smart Cities Mission (SCM) in handling pandemic becomes essential. Hence this paper draws and extends upon Kitchin and Cardullo's "Scaffold of Smart Citizen Participation" through the lens of Latour's Actor-Network Theory, to stress on the aspect of the generalized symmetry within human and non-human actants within Indian smart cities. Through assessments of secondary literature using a hybrid methodology of induction and deduction we draw from

international models of learning and planning aspects of smart cities, to curate a customized conceptual model termed 'Spectrum of Citizen Participation and Inclusion' with a 'Citizen Inclusion Planning Indicator'. This is used to evaluate citizen inclusion for each level of participation, from the perspective of Indian smart cities. This is exemplified through the SCM and COVID-19 pandemic management initiatives keeping the citizens at the core. The analysis highlights an attempt to reimagine the ANT's generalized symmetry to counter the neoliberalist trends of smart cities through a robust participatory turn to the same, and therefore contributing to this realm of STS studies venturing into the aspect of citizen centrality.

Watersheds in India as Emergent Infrastructures: Commoning and Infrastructuring at Different Scales of Governance
Shashank Deora, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai; Pankaj Sekhsaria, Associate Professor, Centre for Technology Alternatives for Rural Areas, Indian Institute of Technol

Watershed (development and management) programmes aiming for natural resource conservation and livelihood generation have been a critical rural development strategy in India for a few decades now. However, the experience of these watershed programmes in India and outside highlights significant social, economic, and political challenges which render the governance of watersheds complex and the replication of these programmes difficult. Significant challenges in watershed governance relate to ensuring equity in cost and benefit distribution and the dynamics across different levels and scales of their governance. This review paper brings together two kinds of literature – commons literature dealing with the large scale complex natural resource governance and infrastructure studies within STS (Science and Technology Studies) – to argue that studying watersheds as emergent infrastructures can facilitate crucial insight into some of the challenges to their governance and their outcomes. It argues that these challenges arise from the interaction of watershed governing institutions, technological interventions within the watershed, and the broader societal context across different scales and levels of their governance. This paper proposes a multi-sited ethnographic investigation into the twin processes of infrastructuring and commoning through watershed programmes to understand watersheds' emergence through these programmes. The approach of studying the intertwined processes of infrastructuring and commoning, which this paper discusses, adds insights from the rich natural resource governance research in the commons literature to study the environmental infrastructure through an STS perspective.

Weapons of the Weak: The Violent Consequences of Biased Technological Change
Aditya Dasgupta, University of California, Merced

Technological change is typically biased, producing wealth that is distributed unequally across groups in society. When the relative losers of technological change lack the political power needed to pursue redistribution through the political system, they may turn to informal and everyday tactics of protest and redistribution -- or "weapons of the weak" -- including violence. The argument is applied to the green revolution in India. The spread of a new crop technology, high-yielding variety (HYV) crops, improved agricultural productivity, but also generated rising inequality between landowners and the rural poor. Drawing on a new historical dataset linking district-level estimates of HYV crop adoption to newly digitized crime records, this paper provides evidence that the spread of the new crop technology during the 1970s and 1980s contributed to a wave of dacoity (banditry), a form of crime that served the function of both small-scale redistribution and social protest against inequality. However, the spread of the new crop technology did not benefit left-wing parties electorally, suggesting that violence was not a precursor to but substitute for

redistribution at the ballot box.

Session Organizers:

Prerna Srigrayan, University of California - Irvine
Misria Shaik Ali, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Discussant:

annapurna mamidipudi, Max Planck Institute for the History of Science

THURSDAY, OCTOBER, 7

159. (Bio)Engineering Nature: Editing environments through biotechnology

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Since the discovery in 2012 of the CRISPR/Cas9 gene editing system, research into its applications has exploded. The use of CRISPR/Cas9 and related technologies has enabled scientists to edit the genomes of organisms with an unparalleled level of accuracy and specificity making feasible the genomic editing of environments and ecosystems. Scientists have pointed out that new technologies like "gene drives", which nearly guarantee the inheritance of targeted genes, could be used for admirable public health goals such as transforming or suppressing harmful populations of malaria transmitting mosquitoes or schistosomiasis-carrying snails. Environmentalists have similarly suggested that gene drives be used to suppress populations of harmful or invasive species, such as lionfish. Theoretically, these technologies appear remarkably promising. Yet, important questions regarding their regulation, usage and development remain underexplored. This panel solicits submissions from groups or individuals of any background interested in developing a rich conversation regarding historical and ongoing attempts to molecularly edit environments with an emphasis on gene drive technologies. Ideally, presenters would explore gene drives in all their complexity, from their social and economic context to their political and environmental implications. This panel would especially welcome papers that document scientific and regulatory processes through which these technologies must go through with a careful attention to empirical detail.

Participants:

Gene Drives and the Coproduction of Nature and Science & Technology
Keje Boersma, Wageningen University, NL;
David Ludwig, Assistant Professor, KTI group, Wageningen University, the Netherlands

Gene drive technologies are marked by certain sociotechnical characteristics that give rise to a particular coproduction dynamic (Jasanoff, 2004; see also Ledingham & Hartley, 2021) of science and technology, conceptions of nature, and views on ethics. We illustrate this dynamic by reflecting on two ethnographies of research groups developing gene drives. Projected gene drive applications are based on the genetic construct's ability to copy itself such that it allows the spreading of genetic alterations through wild populations (Champer et al., 2016). This feature draws conceptions of both nature and ethics deeply into the practices and conversations of laboratories developing gene drives. Regarding the former, our ethnographic work shows how gene drive science is co-constitutive with particular, partly contradictory, conceptions of nature, ranging from biochemistry-based denials of meaningful boundaries in nature to defenses of gene drives on the basis of their "naturalness" and pleas against the technology for interfering with natural processes. Regarding the latter, we show how the concerns about undesirable (accidental, unreflective, unsupervised, unethical) releases of gene drives that emerged immediately together with its initial promises (e.g. Esvelt et al., 2014; Oye et al., 2014; Akbari et al., 2015) and the technology's poster child applications in health (malaria) and conservation (invasive species) (NASEM, 2016) have pulled individual gene drive developers into debates about

the ethics and politics of science and technology. Through the lens of the salience of spatial and temporal scale considerations for gene drives we thus encounter a highly revealing example of how the barriers between laboratory and outside world, micro and macro, and the domains of nature, ethics, science and society are blurred. (word count, excluding references: 240)

REFERENCES Akbari, O.S., Bellen, H.J., Bier, E., Bullock, S.L., Burt, A., Church, G.M., Cook, K.R., Duchek, P., Edwards, O.R., Esvelt, K.M., Gantz, V.M., Golic, K.G., Gratz, S.J., Harrison, M.M., Hayes, K.R., James, A.A., Kaufman, T.C., Knoblich, J., Malik, H.S., Matthews, K.A., O'Connor-Giles, K.M., Parks, A.L., Perrimon, N. Port, F., Russell, S., Ueda, R. & Wildonger, J. (2015) Safeguarding gene drive experiments in the laboratory. *Science*, vol.349, no.6251, pp.927-929. Champer, J., Buchman, A. & Akbari, O.S. (2016) Cheating evolution: engineering gene drives to manipulate the fate of wild populations. *Nature Reviews Genetics*, vol.17, pp.146-159 Esvelt, K.M., Smidler, A.L., Catteruccia, F. & Church, G.M. (2014) Concerning RNA-guided gene drives for the alteration of wild populations. *eLife*, vol.3: e03401. doi: 10.7554/eLife.03401 Jasanoff, S. (ed.) (2004) *States of Knowledge. The co-production of science and social order*. London and New York: Routledge Ledingham, K. & Hartley, S. (2021) Transformation and slippage in co-production ambitions for global technology development: The case of gene drive. *Environmental Science and Policy*, vol.116, pp.78-85 National Academies of Sciences, Engineering, and Medicine (2016) *Gene Drives on the Horizon: Advancing Science, Navigating Uncertainty, and Aligning Research with Public Values*. Washington, DC: The National Academies Press. Oye, K.A., Esvelt, K., Appleton, E., Catteruccia, F., Church, G., Kuiken, T., Lightfoot, S.B-Y., McNamara, J., Smidler, A. & Collins, J.P. (2014) Regulating gene drives. *Science*, vol.345, no.6197, pp.626-628.

Making Gene Drive Comfortable? Negotiating risk governance at the United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity *Sarah Hartley, University of Exeter; Robert David Jonathan Smith, University of Edinburgh; Disha Trivedi, MIT*

Gene drive is a cutting-edge, global and transboundary technology with applications in development in global health, conservation and agriculture. It is controversial and difficult to govern. The United Nations Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD) and its Cartagena Protocol has emerged as a key site in the governance of gene drive, with actors such as the Ad Hoc Technical Expert Group on Risk Assessment, invited parties, governments, indigenous peoples and local communities, exploring whether the technology can be accommodated by established approaches to governance. At the CBD's next major meeting, COP15 and COP/MOP 10 of the Cartagena Protocol, actors will debate whether additional guidance materials on risk assessment are needed to for gene drive organisms. Here, we trace how actors operating within the space of the CBD sought to accommodate gene drive technologies, and the environmental, social and political concerns they are imbricated in, in the 2018-2021 intercessional period. Drawing on Rayner's notion of 'uncomfortable knowledge', we identify how particular topics of debate are more or less easily accommodated within the CBD's governance framework. With particular attention to the uncomfortable topics, we explore the ways in which actors try to make them comfortable. We show how these uncomfortable topics are negotiated and reformatted to make two contributions – one empirical, by unfolding gene drive governance efforts and one theoretical, by expanding the heuristic of uncomfortable knowledge into a case of a global technology governance. This research is funded by a British Academy Award (PI: Hartley; CI: Smith)

The Unbounded Laboratory: Modeling Imaginaries in Gene Drive Research *Marianne Mäkelin, University of Helsinki*
Gene drive mosquitoes are a proposed, in development solution in malaria control. Using the malaria vector mosquitoes

themselves to carry the eradication technology across landscapes is expected to resolve issues of dispersal and sustainability in combatting the disease. This also means, however, that traditional test releases and existing regulatory frameworks cannot be straightforwardly relied upon in assessing the possible path to release for gene drive mosquitoes. This paper examines how the researchers developing gene drive mosquitoes conduct their research amid the conflicting aims of regulatory predictability on one hand and having the mosquitoes spread as wide as possible on the other. Based on interviews with gene drive researchers, it traces the paths taken to produce both gene drive mosquitoes and data about them, and the interplay between field research, laboratory work and mathematical modeling. Connecting with a literature on the contested borders between the laboratory and the field in biological research as well as on landscapes of disease, the paper discusses spatial imaginaries in gene drive research.

Remaking Species, Rethinking Conservation: Taking CRISPR Technologies Seriously Will Change How We See Species *Katrina Maggilli, University of Oregon*

Intensified concern over biodiversity loss has driven recent debate on using CRISPR-Cas9 gene drive technologies as practical solutions for some of the biggest conservation problems. However, seriously considering this clear human intervention into evolutionary processes and species genomes as a conservation tool also reopens deliberation of prior essentialist and normative understandings of species and evolution. This paper analyzes the burgeoning policy-relevant debates on using gene drive technologies in the service of conservation work to argue that seriously considering these technologies as options in conservation reveals the contemporary slippages in popular understandings of species. Where species have been broadly viewed in both policy and popular contexts as genetically delineated, clear entities whose evolutionary changes should never be actively managed by humans, dialogues on altering genetic lineages for the "good" of a species undercuts some of the fundamental assumptions made by traditional conservation models and policies. How conservation biologists and policy makers argue for or against the use of these technologies in conservation reveal particular normative frameworks about what species are and what role humans should play in their evolution—that these normative framings ultimately make their way into conservation practice that actively brings certain worlds into being while preventing others further underscores the ethical fallout of shifting species concepts and the need for confronting their impacts. Analyzing this debate thus contributes directly to broader feminist STS critiques of science's normative and political roles in framing interspecies relationships.

Session Organizer:

Elliott Reichardt, Stanford University

Chair:

Elliott Reichardt, Stanford University

160. Robustness In STS Research Designs And Methods – Making A Difference In Uncertain Worlds? (part 2)

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

STS has a venerable history in generating theoretical concepts and empirical insights into technology. We pride ourselves in avoiding reductionist accounts and opening the black boxes of technological change. Yet our field struggles to provide comprehensive guidance to academics, practitioners and policy makers in neighboring disciplines. This is particularly salient in domains in which STS seeks not only to critique problematic sociotechnical paradigms but also to intervene around social challenges such as climate change mitigation and democratic participation in innovation and design. We propose that one way to enhance the robustness of STS theories and empirical insights is to rethink dominant research designs and study templates. As sociotechnical change is shaped

in many sites and by various social groups, multi-sited studies are needed to allow for the inclusion of actors and modes of knowing rendered invisible by the common investigations of single sites. The uncertainties and contingencies of technological change, in turn, call for longitudinal approaches rather than single snapshot studies. The challenge for STS scholars is how to empirically, methodologically and theoretically “string together” close-up studies of different times and locales with/into broader, longitudinal investigations. Furthermore, how can the insights of these studies be effectively linked to other disciplines and practitioners—who often operate either a more reductionist bird's-eye-view or a piecemeal frog's-eye-view of sociotechnical change? The panel will interrogate these issues from the vantage point of the Biographies of Artifacts and Practices (BoAP) approach that has elaborated a set of tentative responses to the matter.

Participants:

Citizen activities in energy transitions: Tracing the configurational movements to study sociotechnical change
Sampsa Hyysalo, Aalto University

The dominant theorizations of sustainability transitions are anchored to broad-stroke histories and studies of globally early settings of alternative technologies. For understanding how the majority of transitions play out on the ground in specific countries, areas, and locales, these may in fact be rather poor “model organisms”, as most transition dynamics necessarily take place in follower contexts. Analyzing socio-technical change in small scale renewables in Finland through a decade long ethnographic study combined with historical analyses underscores two dynamics. Firstly, transitions in follower contexts are not well characterized as linear diffusion process or quasi-linear social-embedding process. They feature series of configurational movements between global and global and between supply and use during which the materialities, ecologies of actors and interaction arenas become shaped. Second, attention to these configurational movements surfaces actors and activities that have hitherto been invisible or based on theory-led assumptions in birds eye view research. We found citizens to carry out highly important activities in not just adoption but in adaptation and adjustment, user innovation, championing projects, forming user communities, user-side intermediation, market formation, and legitimacy building. These activities continue from the early to the late phases of transition, changing our understanding of relevant actors in energy transitions.

Industrial User Construction: The Concepts of Action Net and Production Device
David Seibt, Technical University of Berlin

In contemporary societies, industries and users are co-constitutive phenomena. We may therefore expect the ongoing digitalization of industrial activities to be related to the transformation of prevalent user roles and identities. Indeed, an extended study of the prosthetics industry demonstrates that the introduction of 3D printing triggered a change of user roles in the field. Yet, available STS concepts are insufficient to fully grasp these transformations. On the one hand, dominant theories concerning the construction of user roles focus on either the activities of technology design or those of technology use. Yet, a narrow focus makes it difficult to account for the interrelation between industries and users throughout the biography of artifacts, such as prosthetic limbs. On the other hand, available theorizing has largely neglected the role of the means of production in mediating the relationship between users and industry. Hence, we are ill-equipped to understand how the introduction of digital technologies, such as 3D printing, may relate to the emergence of new user roles and identities. To address these issues, I will present the concepts of action net and production device. The notion of action net is helpful, because it captures how the repeated interlinking of actions across diverse settings gives rise to a multitude of actorial identities, including those of users, designers, manufacturers, etc. The concept of

production device, in turn, makes visible how the material means of production act as pivotal mediators within action nets that span technology design, distribution, and use.

Orchestration Mechanisms for Innovation in Inverted Firms
Fabio Neves da Rocha, University of Edinburgh; Neil Pollock, The University of Edinburgh

Competition today is progressively fostering innovation processes around digital platforms. As a result, it is argued that organisations are changing the locus where innovation is created: they are ‘inverting the firm’ as innovations now are coming from outside, produced by ecosystem constituents. The orchestration concept – an array of processes that mobilise actors to (co-)innovation – is pivotal to this phenomenon, which some scholars regard as fundamental to the sustainability of digital platforms. Despite such claim, it is unclear how leading digital organisations (such as SAP and Oracle) have successfully orchestrated ecosystem participants in developing complements to their platforms. Combining Information Systems (IS) perspective with insights from Science and Technology Studies (STS), this study offers a socio-technical, longitudinal, and multi-spatial approach. We drew on qualitative data to examine ‘innovation labs’ – an important but yet unstudied space for platform innovation and ecosystem development, showing the mechanisms employed by a global ERP platform leader in the orchestration for innovations that involved customers, startups, independent software vendors (ISVs), systems integrators, and services providers. From there, we derived a model to represent these mechanisms, which we see as interconnected and, in some cases, interdependent. Our analysis of how mechanisms are orchestrated changes the current understanding of platform sustainability, leading us to suggest the nature of innovation as a critical factor rather than the quantity and variety of complements (co-)created.

From the evolution of technological systems to innovation biographies: Exploring the epistemic value of a new metaphor
Eric Lettkemann, Technische Universität Berlin

Metaphors like that of the theater have always inspired sociological thinking. This is also the case in the sociology of technology. In order to explain the dynamics and contingency of technological innovations, many sociologists borrow ideas from concepts of evolutionary biology. Analogous to biological evolution, shaping the development of species by means of natural selection, they conceive the societal environment as a selective entity of technical developments. In this way, sociologists of technology follow a research program that has begun some decades ago in neighboring fields like evolutionary economics or the history of technology. Despite the success of the evolutionary thinking, the metaphor of biological evolution misleads researchers to neglect, in particular, cultural ideas and the reflexivity of human actions that clearly distinguish technical innovations from the blind process of biological evolution. To address this deficiency, I suggest that the sociology of technology should borrow conceptual ideas from biographical research. My paper aims to carve out the additional insights that the metaphor of biographies might provide for the understanding and explanation of technological innovations. To illustrate my arguments, I draw on examples from my own work and other empirical studies that have been conducted in Germany under the label of innovation biographies.

Session Organizers:

Sampsa Hyysalo, Aalto University
Neil Pollock, The University of Edinburgh
David Seibt, Technical University of Berlin
Robin Williams, The University of Edinburgh

161. Diminished Mobility, Reciprocity, Deepening Ties to Place

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Participants:

Looking Through Glass to Explore Good Relations at Home

Maria Eidenskog; Wiktoria Glad, Linköping University

Feelings of homeliness are built on a variety of good relations, such as to the surrounding society, with your family members and the place called home. However, not all buildings are constructed to facilitate good relations for all as individuals have different needs in relationships. In a city district framed as a role model for social sustainability and an inspiration for building designs, shared spaces in wintergardens, large glass windows in homes, laundry rooms and recycling rooms invite some relations, while excluding others. In this paper we will focus on how glass as a building material affect the relations between residents, everyday practices, the neighborhood and the built environment. The increasing use of glass in architecture is an outcome of a reach into the building design from a range of different factors, such as architectural trends, safety measures and social sustainability efforts. Exploring glass through the concept topological reach (Allen, 2016) will make the ontological politics embedded in the building designs visible and in turn show what relations are made possible.

Resisting the Internet: What it was like spending 2020 offline

Aron Lee Rosenberg, McGill

Spending a year without internet was part of a creative candidacy process I completed for the PhD program at McGill University in Montreal. This experiment with refusal came from a place of disagreement – not with the internet, but with an uncritical adoption of the internet that treats its consequences as neutral and its ubiquity as settled. In this paper, I explore how my year offline reoriented my approach to using the internet now that I am back online. Instead of avoiding the internet altogether, I consider how to support the development of a critical/action-oriented collective awareness – what educational activists, following Paulo Freire (1970), call conscientization – in relation to oppressive structures associated with the online world. Living offline provided a context for me to explore how my life and learning are impacted by digital tools. It also gave me an excuse to share my findings in monthly letters to friends and colleagues, and in radio interviews. Navigating the complexities of refusing the internet helped me trace some of the colonial and capitalist relations that normalize and promote certain structures online or that underlie internet usage – often in covert ways through which the user is unknowingly complicit in their own subjugation and in the exploitation of others. This paper considers how my year offline aimed to build collective resistance and prefigure more responsible digital praxes. Getting back online, I contend that using the internet critically can be realized through and as direct actions that reorient our relationships to digital and online spaces.

Staying afloat: relating to/from the Landwehr canal and other slow epistemologies

Baldeep Grewal, University of Potsdam
This paper draws on my experience as a neurodiverse person who moved to Berlin just as the city went into lockdown in March 2020, and as a researcher grappling with their increasingly impossible project. Working from within the disorienting event of a pandemic, I will discuss the Landwehr canal along two vectors: slow mobilities and notions of safety. Learning from Sara Ahmed's concept of orientation, I illustrate how the canal became a site for re-orienting oneself within a locked-down city using my field notes and photographs from kayak trips, and from observing the canal from my window. Moving through the canal reveals slow epistemologies of urban space: submerged objects (scooters, bicycles, shopping carts), magnetic fishing events, how the canal relates to the river, non-verbal misunderstandings with people on the banks, finding hidden graffiti, and using bridges to tell time and distance. Building this optimistic relationship included reckoning with my previous canal-relations from growing up in India: canals as colonial legacy, pollution bearers and reminders of personal loss. In Berlin, as people began to

meet in and around the canal, ever-changing practices of safe(ly) unfolded where water became a technique of simultaneous socializing and social distancing. Engaging with STS research on mobilities, nonhuman relations and media, I will talk about the effect of slowness on orientation techniques and the media environments of kayaks.

(Why) Does It Matter That I'm Also Here If We're Both On Zoom?

Elizabeth Resor, UC Berkeley School of Information

In this paper I reflect on the locational and methodological shifts in my dissertation research necessitated by the pandemic. Instead of continuing an ethnographic project in Kenya, I shifted to a remotely conducted interview study in Oakland, California (where I currently live). The switch from site-based ethnographic methods to online and remote approaches forced me to consider more closely how I had addressed my positionality as a researcher with my initial methodological choices, and to acknowledge how daily life practices constituted acts of research and reciprocity that needed to be replicated or substituted with online and remote action. Despite these differences, this forced shift also illuminated how many of my commitments as a researcher have not changed, and in fact, that bringing in decolonial practices from my previous work can help me regain what I felt I had lost in moving away from ethnographic methods. Given that both projects relate to how understandings of place are expressed in online activity and information, there is also a secondary meditation on how place is expressed during online interactions – including those between researcher and research participant.

Session Organizer:

Sam Coren, Brown University

162. STS in/from/and Asia

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Since Daiwie Fu first asked 'how far can East Asian STS go?' in the inaugural issue of *East Asian Science, Technology and Society* in 2007, many scholars have considered the limits and possibilities of STS in the Asian region. This open panel seeks to build on these conversations, drawing on empirical studies of technoscience within, across and beyond Asia. A persistent theme in explorations of STS and Asia has been the troubling of critiques based on west/non-west binaries, recognizing instead processes of creolization, hybridity and syncretism in both technoscience and in STS scholarship. As the centre of geopolitical gravity shifts to what is increasingly called the Indo-Asia-Pacific, Asia is the site of novel imaginaries and bold experimentation in every aspect of 21st century life - from energy transition to biosecurity to gene editing to surveillance capitalism – that are shaped by intersecting legacies of European and Asian colonialisms, ongoing Indigenous dispossession and persecution of minority groups, ecological collapse and acute vulnerability to climate change. Contributing to discussions that have begun through the new TransAsiaSTS Network, we seek papers on all aspects of technoscience that contribute to answering questions such as: What can STS offer the study of technoscience in Asia and what does Asia offer STS? What kind of categories are 'STS in Asia' or 'Asian STS'? How do they relate to Indigenous, queer, feminist, postcolonial, decolonial, and posthuman inflections of STS scholarship? How can scholarly infrastructures better support STS research and research training in the region? How can collaborations in the region contribute to building solidarities and strengthening civil societies? How might these in turn inform practical efforts on the ground? What possibilities can emerge from comparisons of STS in/from/and Asia and other regional formations, located in Northern as well as Southern contexts?

Participants:

GenomeAsia100K: Leveraging Asian DNA to Build National Science in Singapore *Manoj Vimal, Nanyang Technological University*

Large population-based genomic studies have until now focussed mainly on European ancestral populations. The Singapore-based

GenomeAsia100K (GA100K) Consortium aims to address this underrepresentation by targeting major Asian populations and generating reference genomes for each ethnic group. GA100K is also studying historical population migrations and providing bioinformatic tools that may help tackle diseases among Asia's multi-ethnic populations. These project goals transcend national boundaries, national genome projects, or localized national science, and medicine. Rather, GA100K leverages the strategic location of Singapore as a regional nexus to advance science and technology within Singapore. GA100K is thus symptomatic of the Singaporean nation-state's ambition to be a knowledge-based economy and a regional biomedical hub. This article thus contributes to literature in STS that deals with the inter-connections of human tissue biobanks, human genomic projects, and national development.

Hong Kong as Unintended Gatekeeper of China's Wayward Science *Harry Yi-Jui Wu*

When mentioning STS in Asia, one tends to ignore significance of Hong Kong as predominantly a commercial city. Using the sensational case of genome-edited babies revealed in 2018 at a conference in Hong Kong, this paper explores the role of "Asia's World City" as the very site for "novel imaginaries and bold experimentation" to occur. In this presentation, I argue that the incident of the first CRISPR-ed babies born in China has not yet been closed. Doubtful points have not yet been fully clarified despite the Chinese court had ruled He Jiankui being guilty in 2019. During the painstaking organizing process before the genome-editing summit, Hong Kong's ambiguous status became a suitable venue to accommodate controversy. The city had been aspiring itself to become a hub of technology and innovation since the millennium. However, the rapidly drafted plan did not map out clear directions for the city to follow, including ethical guidelines in scientific research. Now, with China's cutting-edge science being fervently developed unrestrictedly, the He Jiankui storm became a trial balloon floated into the air to sound out professional as well as public opinions. On one hand, the incident implies that Hong Kong's unique position and its prosperous, free, transparent, and safe conditions it could maintain have carved itself a potential role gate keep Chinese wayward scientific and technological development. On the other hand, the city might continue to suffer from the awkward silence it has to maintain regarding ethical agenda whilst being gradually absorbed into China's growing "techranny".

Speaking into the archive: science podcast in India *Usha Raman, University of Hyderabad*

The continuing push to decolonize and re-appropriate histories of various kinds has in recent years found resonance in multiple narrative forms, from popular non-fiction to museum exhibits to documentary film, and most lately, podcasts. In the podcasting space, there have been several notable efforts to build alternative stories of science and technology in India, combining a critical view with a commitment to go beyond dominant Western-influenced narratives. Among these are the now discontinued *Intersections*, *Desi Stones and Bones*, and *Scrolls & Leaves*. Disavowing the more political move to recall the lost glory of a precolonial past, or a celebration of an ancient history of innovation, these narratives take a systematic look at overlooked aspects of scientific and technological phenomena that have their moorings in—or connections to the Indian subcontinent. While these popular media forms position themselves as non-fiction storytelling, they serve as an important archive-in-the-making, often themselves drawing on newly built repositories (such as the archive of the National Institute of Biological Sciences in Bengaluru). Drawing on an analysis of selected podcasts, combined with interviews with producers and archivists, this paper seeks to understand the interpretive frameworks that underlie the production of these narratives, arguing that they represent important attempts to resituate and decenter histories of science and technology in the subcontinent while resisting the

cultural nationalism that permeates much of political discourse.

Denying Darwinism in Korea: STS and Creationism in a Developmental State *Hyung Wook Park, Nanyang Technological University*

More than 30 percent of South Koreans confessed their creationist belief and denied evolution in recent surveys. Hence, the historian of science Ronald Numbers has called the country "the creationist powerhouse" alongside the United States. This talk discusses a key facet of this religious belief. I analyze how South Korean creationists with scientific training have used the history, philosophy, and sociology of science – broadly defined as "STS" – in denial of a major scientific fact, evolution. Admittedly, this work is not original, because it stems from American creationists' strategy of relativizing science to deny the epistemic validity of Darwinism. Robert Pennock and Michael Ruse thus criticized Steve Fuller and others who argued that evolution might not be true because it was "socially constructed." But this appropriation assumed a new connotation in South Korea's context. Borrowing cases from history, philosophy, and STS in challenging evolutionary theory, Korean creationists were able to deviate from their country's conventional focus on technological prowess. As the scholarship in history, philosophy, and sociology was deemed relevant to the humanities, the creationists, who were educated in technical disciplines, could identify themselves as Christian literati (*chisigin*) responsible for a broad array of topics regarding morality and politics that supposedly belonged only to the country's leaders trained in liberal arts. This new identification has been significant in Korea, a developmental state with a Confucian background that rigorously disciplined and controlled scientific professionals for its international competitiveness. Defending their faith through STS, the creationists resisted their country's major agendas.

Upturning the Energy Ladder: Ritual Purity and Air Pollution in India *Deepti Chatti, Humboldt State University*

Household air pollution, or the smoke from cooking fires, is seen as a grave risk to the health and well-being of low-income rural families in India, and a way that the world's poor contribute to global climate change. Sustainable development organizations and state actors attempt to facilitate just and sustainable energy transitions as a way to mitigate the environmental, social, and public health costs of so-called "traditional" cookstoves. Development actors who work on facilitating a clean energy transition in low-income homes in the global South speak of an "energy ladder" of progress. The ladder stacks technologies and fuels from "clean" to "dirty", and graphs that against the wealth of the household. By ethnographically analyzing energy transitions in low-income rural Indian homes, my research and provides two critiques of dominant development narratives. First, my research shows that emic conceptions of a life well-lived include multiple energy and cooking technologies, including the so called "dirty" and "traditional" stove. Furthermore, families that use traditional stoves use it because of its association with health and well-being. These ideas of well-being are dependent not simply on the particulate matter concentrations in the air (the smoke from cooking fires) but on individual and community understandings of good cooking, eating, and spatial and temporal practices relating to caste and gender relations in rural Himachal Pradesh. In addition to 18 months of ethnographic fieldwork in India in collaboration with community-based organizations, I draw upon my role as a social scientist and participant-observer in a randomized control trial (RCT) on cookstove adoption and air pollution carried out by a consortium of researchers in the US and Canada. My research extends beyond critically studying the technologies and programs designed to facilitate clean energy transitions to also include the politics of knowledge involved in conducting transnational research with historically marginalized communities for informing and facilitating global energy transitions.

Web standards and Protocols: Identifying Transnational Actors and Networks *Chinar Mehta*

Research about ICTs in the discipline of communication has primarily focussed on their deployment for development, particularly in Asia. However, there are significant research issues regarding the development of ICTs themselves and the hybrid collaborations that occur between corporations, states, and other organizations that go beyond the binary of West or non-West. For these issues, the approach from the cultural studies of science which situates scientific practice in a legacy of colonial projects ongoing with the help of state and corporate power, can be relevant. Largely, web standardisation practices have emerged in the US and Europe, but collaborations between standards developing organizations, governments, and other non-profit or for-profit organizations structure web standards and protocols, thereby structuring the Web. Additionally, web standards, protocols, and tools are intermediate ICTs in the production of other ICTs, the development of which is not limited to where and how the standards develop. Identifying relevant actors in such diffused decision-making circumstances is a significant challenge. In this paper, I center web technologies to expand on these collaborations. Holding suspect the discourse of “free information access” has been prevalent in post-colonial studies of communication, and STS provides theoretical frameworks to historicize and contextualise these web standards. To that end, this paper offers methodological possibilities to identify diverse actors in the domain of web standards and protocols that seem to have unique arrangements of networks that cannot be described simply by geography or location.

Session Organizers:

Emma Kowal, Deakin University
Aalok Khandekar, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad
Lyle Fearnley, Singapore University of Technology and Design
Usha Raman, University of Hyderabad
Hsin-Hsing Chen, Shih-Hsin University Graduate Institute for Social Transformation Studies

Chair:

Lyle Fearnley, Singapore University of Technology and Design

Discussant:

Itty Abraham, National University of Singapore

163. Aspiring Societal Impact. The Epistemological Politics of Interventionist Research in STS - II

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:

Behind the Screens: The Political Prehistory of the Sociology of Science and the Neoliberal Frustration of Science *William T. Lynch, Wayne State University*

Science and Technology Studies has struggled with the issue of the public use of symmetrical treatment of controversies at least since Scott, Richards and Martin (1990), who worried that the losing side of science-based controversies appealed to the sociologist’s analysis to try to revive their case. Since then, a shift in rhetoric from neutrality to relevance has led some away from a concern about being captured by underdogs to an effort to actively capture clients who need epistemic rehabilitation. At the same time, the field has worried about the abuse of scientific uncertainty by powerful industries to derail regulation. Discussion of the implications that a social interpretation of science has for democratic society has historical precedents in the prehistory of our field. Recent historical work on early figures such as Michael Polanyi, Otto Neurath, Boris Hessen, J. D. Bernal, Robert Merton, Karl Lazarsfeld, and Theodor Adorno show that they addressed concerns similar to our own over post-truth, expertise, and the neoliberal corruption of science. These debates have been distorted by decontextualized readings and an

exaggerated emphasis on our field’s theoretical novelty.

Common to both their context and ours is concern about the impact that new mass media technologies and commercialism have on democracy and science. I consider the “frustration of science” brought on by today’s neoliberal and client-centered science and the challenges posed for scientific institutions by growing distrust in experts.

Cultivating Space and Propagating Questions: Reimagining the Interview as a Site of Science Studies Intervention *Rebecca Harrison, Cornell University*

Agricultural scientists today are acutely aware of public concerns around genetic engineering, which range from questions about human and environmental safety to corporatization of the food supply. Alongside development of new generations of agricultural biotechnologies, many scientists therefore find themselves creatively navigating various biological and social boundaries. Their goal is to cultivate support for their work through different, oftentimes innovative means. This paper seeks to further understand how academic scientists at land-grant universities, with their explicitly public focus, adapt their work with controversial technologies to meet multiple scientific and public goals. Preliminary work shows that when provided with the opportunity, many scientists are willing, and indeed interested, to reflect on their roles, responsibilities, and the meanings of their work. Rather than providing after-the-fact analysis, this project seeks to yield a model of embedded social science research that encourages scientists to think critically about ethical impacts of their work in real-time. This paper places a collection of detailed portraits of university scientists within the deeply intertwined histories of the land-grant university, of democratic professionalism, of the political economy of biotechnology, and of the scientific ideas of control and responsibility. By conducting this research in collaboration with scientists themselves, this project seeks to demonstrate a way for science studies experts to engage productively with the scientific community, positioning scholars to nudge scientific practice in more thoughtful, subtly interventionist directions.

Impacts for Whom? Assessing Inequalities in NSF-funded Broader Impacts Using the Immediacy Inclusion Criterion *Sophia Boutilier, Stony Brook University*

Accounting for the value of scientific research through broader impacts (BI) and responsible innovation has generated debate on the purpose of science and measuring the impact of research and development (R&D). However, what is often overlooked is to whom are the impacts directed. In this paper we review common impact metrics and introduce a new framework, the Immediacy Inclusion Criterion (IIC). The IIC assesses who benefits from research impacts as divided into three groups: (1) advantaged groups; (2) the general population with no specific target group; and (3) marginalized groups that are typically excluded. In the study we analyze project outcome reports (POR) from the National Science Foundation (NSF) and find that advantaged groups are the most likely to benefit from NSF-funded research. We also show that certain areas of research (as distinguished by the NSF directorates) are more efficient at generating impacts for marginalized groups. We further argue that persistent inequalities in broader impacts of scientific research limit the potential of R&D to increase prosperity and well-being.

Session Organizer:

Jitse Schuurmans, Erasmus University Rotterdam

Chair:

Dara Ivanova, Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management

Discussants:

Iris Wallenburg, institute for Health Policy and Management
Roland Bal, Erasmus University Rotterdam

164. Becoming with Water: Ethnographic and Methodological

Reconfigurations — I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

How does water reterritorialize the very grounds that seem to stabilize the claims of modern states and capitalist endeavors? The papers in this panel examine the spatial orders that emerge from water's innate capacity to defy, refuse or exceed technoscientific attempts to render shores, coasts and borders into fixed entities. Drawing methodologically on water's fluidity, the authors of this panel attend to the multiscale ways in which water plays with land to perturb the stability of the land-water binary. Transporting us to coasts and shorelines, meandering with rivers and borders, the authors ask what it means to rethink territorial formations through a watery lens. By placing water at the heart of emerging cartographies, the authors trace its flows to remap STS scholarship on infrastructures, surveillance and the production of landscapes.

Participants:

Flowing water and passing time: Thinking through urban rivers in Addis Ababa, Ethiopia *Cady Gonzalez, University of Florida Department of Anthropology*

Rivers of mud washing away homes and erupting over bridges. Water trickling through beds of stone, concrete rubble and plastic bottles. As the space where the waste and excess of the city seep in, coagulate and mount up, rancid riverbeds have held the streets of Addis Ababa, Ethiopia in their noxious grip for decades. While rivers seem to flow forward, mirroring the linearity of time, French philosopher Michel Serres reminds us that as they encounter other material bodies, they double back in eddying currents that percolate flows and push some of the present back into the past. This paper juxtaposes two river tributaries and their terrains to ask: What does the variable flow of an urban river system gather and return to? What then is forgotten? As riverways collect territories, what political and legal relations do they entwine? Which relations sediment and which pass with the current? Drawing upon twelve months of fieldwork in 2019, I gather diverse voices, terrains and histories from two riverside parks that at different times are prone to accumulation, and others, tend toward erosion. In doing so, I illustrate how the varied, multifarious and unpredictability of rivers and their territories echo the instability and heterogeneity of Ethiopian political relations, past and present.

Lines in the Sand: Precarious Property on Ghana's Eroding Coast *Netty Carey, University of Florida Department of Anthropology*

In 2013, Government of Ghana (GoG) leased land in Kedzi, a Volta estuary fishing village, to Trasacco Estates Development Company Ltd. (TEDC) for resort and marina development. As the plans of this Italian-Ghanaian firm move forward, bolstered by a partnership with Hilton Worldwide, Kedzi's 1200 residents refuse promised relocation. Having endured numerous erosion-induced displacements, they struggle to maintain their claim on the land that remains. This paper thus traces the contours of claims on a land that is inseparable from the water that surrounds it. Using the words and stories of the people of Kedzi, I explore the reciprocal landscape that emerges through a lived history of cyclical shorelines and daily movements in and out of water. Sand accretes and accumulates with the tides; is heaped, dredged, mined, obstructed, and flattened by a state intent on controlling the water's movements to save habitats and make profitable property. With each change of this shifting sandscape, residents, entrepreneurs, chiefs, developers, and bureaucrats reterritorialize the land that emerges. This history highlights the difficulty of defining property lines in a place where the boundary between land and water is perpetually in flux. While this poses challenges for efforts to convert land into a transactable thing of value, residents find political possibility in the churning newness of a landscape perpetually reborn.

Dredging for Common Grounds: Remaking River-Depth at

Coastal Chennai *Oviya Govindan, University of California Irvine*

This paper examines the shifting cultural meanings associated with the socio-technical practice of dredging at coastal Chennai. On the one hand, dredging is often tied to practices of extractive relations to subterranean grounds like river-beds and estuarine beds. For instance, the tagline on the website of International Seaport Dredging, a contractor in Chennai reads, "Creating Land for the future", and dredging the coastline involves excavating sediments and sands in the riverbeds and sea-bed to make coastal natures anew. On the other hand, in coastal Chennai, dredging is also potent with possibilities for a restorative future. In a context where industrial substances have made rivers and estuaries in coastal Chennai unnavigable, social movements in contemporary coastal Chennai call for the year-round dredging of estuaries to keep water flowing and prevent flooding in the future. I examine these tensions in the histories of dredging as extraction and restoration by bringing ethnographic data into conversation with coastal engineering literatures. In particular, I engage with STS literatures on the materiality of water and watery spaces like deltas and coastlines (Bhattacharya 2019; Krause 2017), on geo-social relations and emergent politics of ground and underground spaces (Ballesterio 2016; Sur and Kerr 2019; Klinger 2015; Cons 2017), and discard studies approaches to repair and waste (Liboiron, Tironi and Calvillo 2018).

Fixing the Tide: Mapping and Fishing the Salty Shore *Chitra Venkataramani*

This paper looks at how India's new coastal policy maps its near-shore waters and its consequences for fishing communities and the nonhumans that inhabit Mumbai's edge. The policy reconfigures the fluid space of the shore into distinct zones and introduces new pressures on the dynamic field in which fishers operate and fish spawn. In order to legitimize these regimes of coastal management, the state has to first determine the boundaries of the coast through coastal surveys. In this drawing process, nonhumans such as berms, dunes, and particularly salt, or salinity, act as signifiers that demarcate new territories in the liminal space where land and sea meet. These elements often resist interpretation through the many unexpected ways in which they behave or appear, making it difficult to delineate new boundaries and zones. The paper attends to the ways in which the cartographic pursuits of coastal management attempt to draw water, papering over the ambiguities and conundrums caused by nonhuman agency, and in the process, remake coastal futures.

Session Organizer:

Shweta Krishnan, George Washington University

Chair:

Dana Burton, George Washington University

165. From Social Science OF Science to Social Science WITH Science in Studying Food

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Our panel seeks to query the opportunities and challenges of radical interdisciplinarity, moving from a social science OF science, observing the social implications of science, towards a social science WITH science, where social sciences are brought into and invited to inform the sciences they study. The papers in this panel query the messy, uneasy, and yet highly inspiring and mutually enriching relations that such radical interdisciplinary can entail. Hannah Landecker discusses her collaboration as a social scientist with a biogeochemist in the study of the (historic) lifelines of methionine, an amino acid, starting as an additive in animal feed and subsequently entering through the food chain into the human diet. Erica Jansen and Elizabeth Roberts report on how the collaboration between a nutritional epidemiologist and ethnographer on the 'nutrition transition' enabled them to deploy two discipline-specific methodologies that proved insightful for each other and moved their joint project forward. Three papers discuss collaborations by social scientists with food and gut

microbiota researchers. The first, by Joshua Evans, Rob Dunn and Jamie Lorimer, develops an interdisciplinary participatory approach for co-producing microbiological knowledge involving culinary professionals, and social and natural scientists. Papers by Wim Van Daele and Raul Tadeo, and by Amber Benezra, ponder experiences of specific collaborations between social anthropologists and gut microbiome scientists, with the former focusing on the process of co-designing a research project and integrating contradictory disciplinary demands, and the latter building on a rich experience of an anthropology of microbiomes, discussing the uneasy partnerships this entails.

Participants:

From Archives to Isotopes: Studying the Transit of Petroleum-derived Nutrients Through Social and Biological Worlds
Hannah Landecker, UCLA

This talk reflects on a collaboration between social science and biogeochemistry in the investigation of nutrients made directly from fossil fuels. Our example is methionine, an essential amino acid for humans and animals, which is also an important commodity in the global animal feed market. Approximately 1 million tons of methionine are synthesized yearly from petroleum for use in animal feed. The implications of a synthetic input of methionine into the world food supply have not been systematically studied, and little is known about the fate of methionine in animal feed as it moves through the food chain into the human diet. This paper lays the groundwork for studying synthetic methionine in the food supply, exploring the origins of synthetic methionine in the chemical industry, establishing historical data on production trends since the mid-twentieth century, and modeling the movement of synthetic methionine from animal feed into humans as meat and animal product consumption changes.

A Bioethnography of Eating in Mexico City
Erica Jansen, University of Michigan; Elizabeth Roberts, University of Michigan

The story of the nutrition transition goes like this – “traditional” plant and grain-based diets have shifted to more “Westernized” diets, high in sugars and saturated fat, leading to rising rates of obesity and chronic disease. Nutritional epidemiologists use food factor analysis to statistically understand the impact of the nutrition transition on population-level health outcomes. They examine how individuals tend to eat certain foods together in patterned ways, naming them, “Prudent”, “Traditional”, “Unhealthy”, and “Westernized, etc.” This paper describes how a nutritional epidemiologist and an ethnographer sought to combine food factor analysis and ethnographic data from a longitudinal environmental health study in Mexico City. They wanted to develop a more complex understanding of how study participants eat than was possible for each method on its own. Initially, the food factor data revealed “traditional” and “Westernized” patterns. When combined with the ethnographic data however, it appeared that these patterns might have little to do with individual choice or a dietary transition. Instead, individual differences in eating depended on whether a participant’s family was economically stable or not. Both economically stable and unstable families ate a lot of “western foods” but the economic capacity to have a large and varied, mid-day meal made the individuals from those families appear “prudent” and “traditional”. To the ethnographer’s surprise, food factor analysis provided a useful means to document this crucial economic difference. The ethnographer was also pleased to contribute to an epidemiological paper arguing that nutritional naming practices might foreclose our understanding of how people eat.

Towards a Public Science of Fermentation and the Food Microbiome
Joshua Evans, University of Oxford; Rob Dunn, University of Copenhagen; Jamie Lorimer, University of Oxford

Researchers have long been interested in the exchange of microbes through the production and the consumption of food. Much is now known about the risks posed by foodborne microbial pathogens. Much less is known about the role of human-sourced microbes in fermentation and how foodborne microbes shape a healthy microbiome. Such mutualistic exchanges have long been a part of vernacular cooking practice and continue unremarked in many parts of the world. But they have become a topic of growing interest in the Western food system in context of growing anxieties about the health effects of missing microbes and the rise of ‘post-Pasteurian’ (Paxson 2012) approaches to food preparation. In this paper we outline an interdisciplinary approach for doing social science with science that is conjoined with a participatory methodology for engaging fermenters with microbes. We develop a three-way model for the co-production of microbiological knowledge involving culinary practitioners with social and natural scientists. Our model aims to both democratise the tools of metagenomics and to let the concerns of social scientists and chefs shape the emerging scientific research agenda around the food microbiome. We present findings from research projects with culinary fermenters in the New Nordic Cuisine, an international group of professional bakers convened in Belgium, and home-cook citizen scientists in the UK and identify key research questions for a public science of fermentation and the food microbiome.

Decentering Gut Microbiota in Sri Lanka Through an Anthropology with Microbiology
Wim Van Daele, University of Agder; Raul Yhossef Tito Tadeo, KU Leuven

Recent research on gut microbiomes has taken the social scientists’ imagination by storm. As the composition of the gut microbiota is profoundly influenced by ‘environmental’ factors, comprising both natural and anthropogenic exposures, the hope is that this research will reveal bi-directional, causal pathways across the age-old nature/nurture divide. Whereas in social sciences of science approaches, gut microbiomes are studied in terms of their socio-cultural import and ethical quandaries that may emerge around this science, we discuss our efforts to arrive at a social science with science approach where the disciplinary habituses of an anthropologist and a gut microbiome scientist aim to encounter each other in an integrated research design. This encounter inspired our choice to conduct research on the gut microbiota composition among two ethnic groups in Sri Lanka and to explore how these are shaped by culturally informed food production and consumption, whereby we seek to decenter and pluralize the universalizing biology grounded in Euro-American biological material and bodies often taken as the biomedical standard. We will query the difficulties we have encountered in setting up such a research design that weds the required standards for a decent in-depth ethnography with the microbiological requirement to obtain sufficient samples for making defensible claims grounded in bio-statistically relevant correlations. We also discuss additional challenges in integrating these disciplinary requirements in Sri Lankan bodies. We conclude by programmatically discussing key elements of the research design we believe have solved some the key tensions in becoming a project of social science with science.

Microbiome Ethnographers
Amber Benezra, Stevens Institute of Technology

Human microbiomes inextricably entangle biology with social, intimate practices, and consequently the study of human microbial ecology also entangles the bio and social sciences. Microbes are a vector of coevolution across life forms and between disciplines. This paper asks then, what would it mean for anthropology to act with science? What I call anthropology of microbes operationalizes ethnographic knowledge, asking us to be ethnographers of and for microbiome research, facing the corresponding compromises and uncertainties, challenges and failures. Rather than mere observational fieldwork among scientists, an anthropology of microbes requires anthropologists

to become members of scientific teams and contribute ethnographic data, while requiring biological scientists to make space in research design, experimentation, and implementation for social science expertise and thinking. These transdisciplinary collaborations are not easy; the anthropological stakes are continuously offset and commingled with questions of health, illness, and biology, as well as highly technical data. Asymmetries of power, anger and frustration abound. An anthropology of microbes is a circuit of collaboration that must deal with gender, class, race, geographic and epistemic boundaries; and unfocuses the lines of individual, personal, and professional agency. I attempt to move transdisciplinary engagement beyond ethical policing, theoretical backbiting, and critical observation, towards action. Feminist STS theory and ethnography may be able to provide both structural and local context for biomedical intervention, while social scientists learn to take material biology and the corresponding science seriously. An anthropology of microbes aims to transform human microbial ecology and anthropology through the operation of uneasy partnerships.

Session Organizer:

Wim Van Daele, University of Agder

Chair:

Heather Paxson, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Discussant:

Jörg Niewöhner, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin

166. The Postcolonial Politics of Election Technologies – I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

The benefits and costs of election technologies (voting machines, biometric voter registration and authentication, electronic transmission of results) are now much debated. Despite the criticisms, high-tech voting systems are booming in many parts of the world: for example, half of the countries in Africa have adopted biometrics for voter registration procedures. This panel aims to investigate the transnational circulation of these technologies and the invention of new markets in Africa, Asia and Latin America. Particular attention should be paid to the neoliberal and postcolonial logics underlying the spread of these technologies. Who plays a major role in the roll-out of election technologies in the Global South? To what extent are countries in Africa and elsewhere used as a testing ground by the private companies providing the technologies? We aim to explore the strategies of old and new actors in this field: election commissions, ICT and biometric experts, private firms. A second key objective of this panel is to make sense of the practical effects of election technologies in the countries concerned. In many countries, the technologies have raised high expectations. How do governments, political opponents as well as activists strategically use them? How does the collection of data transform electoral politics and the architecture of the state? As lawyers and privacy advocates face major challenges, perspectives from the Global South and battles fought there are also crucial for the rest of the world. Ultimately, this panel explores how election technologies have shaped our contemporary practice and politics of democracy.

Participants:

From Marbles to Papers: “Pragmatism,” Post-Colonial Identity, and the Gains of Democracy in The Gambia’s Electoral System *Niklas Hultin*, *George Mason University*

This paper examines the debate in the Gambia around the country’s shift from its distinctive marble/bells/drum voting system to a conventional paper ballot system announced in 2020. It examines the origins and argument for the “marble” system, tracing it to its creation in 1960 during the colonial era up through today, as well as the arguments against it (e.g. cost and a kind of national embarrassment at not having a more mainstream or “modern” voting system). Drawing on long-term ethnographic research in the Gambia, the paper puts this debate in the context of several profound shifts of 2010s The Gambia, namely a) the contested shift to a democratic system after the autocratic rule of

Yahya Jammeh; b) the rise of biometric identification, including a scandal in the Gambia about shortage of identity documents and the corrupt awarding of foreign contracts for biometric identification under Jammeh; c) the abrupt shift from recognizing China (PRC) instead of Taiwan (the latter carried the considerable expense of the marbles, since they had to be replaced for each election). Nonetheless, the paper argues that the debate about the election system is only peripherally about cost but about the legitimacy of process that semi-realized the Gambia’s hard earned democracy and worries about throwing away the symbolic vehicle of that gain.

The electronic transmission of results in Latin America : a « black box »? *Erica Guevara*

On May 20, 2018, Gustavo Petro, a presidential candidate in Colombia, denounced a risk of electoral fraud due to the software intended to transmit the results of the polling stations to the public institution which centralized the results. At the heart of his argument, the idea that the software subcontracted to private and foreign companies, was a “black box”, which escaped the control of the public institutions guaranteeing the election. This “scandal” became a central issue for election observation missions, which received detailed presentations from technicians from public institutions, aimed to reassure observers. According to the technicians, fraud was impossible, because pieces of evidence in the old paper format guaranteed all stages of the electoral process. Similar incidents have occurred recently in other countries in the region that have used results transfer tools and applications, such as Ecuador, Costa Rica, and Brazil. Seen as a guarantee of greater efficiency (because allowing to reduce “human errors”), the use of technologies planned to transmit the results of the vote also introduces an element of opacity and “magic” in the process. Based on the literature on the socio-history of the vote and on the construction of electoral truth, and empirical data from the participant observation of electoral observation missions in Colombia, Ecuador, and Costa Rica, this paper analyzes the processes of politicization and commodification of the transmission of results in Latin America.

Winning elections through the debacle of technologies: A study on Nigeria’s general elections *Opeyemi Aluko*

Almost all countries in the world conduct periodic elections. Many of them have adopted the use of new technologies to improve the acceptability of the election outcome, facilitate the conduct of elections and improve the desired outcomes. Election technology is not alien to the developed countries unlike the developing countries. In the developing countries, especially in Nigeria, election technologies were deployed for the 2015 and 2019 general elections. The reason behind the deployment of such election technologies is not different as such from that of the developed country. However, further analysis reveals that the technologies have either promoted the agenda of the few educated electorates or opened a new dimension in cheating or manipulation of vote. The possibilities of a deliberate calibration of election machines to function in a certain manner from the manufacturers in conjunction with the importers in African countries cannot be jettisoned. Election technologies can as well be a tool in the hands of the developed countries to test their new technology at the expense of an entire country’s stability. Therefore, what are the dimensions of strength and weakness of the use of election technologies in countries like Nigeria? Have these technologies preconditioned the process and the outcome of the elections in Nigeria? What is the role of the technology manufacturers? The dependency theory will be used in the study to explain the effects of the new election technologies on the development in Nigeria as a precursor for developing countries.

Session Organizer:

Marielle Debos, Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton

Chair:

Cecilia Passanti, University of Paris

167. Latin American Men in Feminism: Social Studies of the Production of Knowledge - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Participants:

Beware of the Trojan Horse: Discussing Risk and Support in Mexican Institutions *Luisa Fernanda Grijalva Maza, International Relations Department, UPAEP Universidad*

In the last few years, feminist movements in Latin America have acquired notoriety both locally and internationally. In this context, the question about the role of men has had an important place in the discussions within the myriad of feminisms in LA, especially, when encountering the idea of feminist men. Although there are many positions that try to tackle this difficult question, in this paper I discuss particularly the problem of risk in Mexico within one institution of knowledge production. It is widely known that femicide is a deep and growing problem in Mexico, which has allowed not only the expansion of feminist movements, but also the appearance of “allies” or “feminist men” or “men that support women” (these titles are not the same and carry different political commitments) that position themselves against the horrifying physical violence that plagues the lives of women. At the same time, the political position against femicide has also allowed the idea of being “feminist” or “ally” or “men that support women” to become a sort of “title” that institutions and some men within those institutions have appropriated as a politically correct position. This, of course, is a very limited feminism because, as I show here, it is against the murder of women because of their gender but has no intention of bringing down the patriarchal structures that make femicide possible. In this sense, the issue has to do with risk both from the perspective of men and women. Risk, not only physical but emotional and epistemological, in the workplace is a reality discussed within feminist scholars (in this case, in universities). Given that women continue to be an economically vulnerable group in Mexico, risk of losing jobs or being blacklisted or being punished is a present danger for women that seek to further feminist agendas or that look for protection from violence in or outside the workplace. In the case of men and institutions, risk plays a different role -it functions as a thermometer or mediator to set limits to the support they are willing to provide to women. As I show here with one specific case, as long as the title of “ally” did not risk the privileged position of men, the university and its departments were all for the movements. Yet, when women took things a bit further, the departments and the institutions closed ranks. This is not to say that men have no place in feminist movements, yet, a deep discussion of risk requires further scrutiny in Mexican institutions, especially, the need to share risk at an institutional level.

New Roles for Latin American Men in Feminism? *Sandra Harding, Graduate Department of Education, UCLA*

There have always been men who advanced the conditions of their daughters, wives, others, employees, friends and colleagues. Women's social justice movements have always identified distinctive tasks for men who would support such movements--tasks that only men can perform because of their positions in social relations as men. Today new social justice movements aimed entirely or at least partly at improving women's lives have emerged: Me Too, Black Lives Matter, and new environmental approaches, for example. What have been the distinctive tasks for men that each has identified? How have such projects played out in Latin America, where continuing machismo ideals and practices often have had violent effects on women's lives. What are the valuable STS research and policy questions here?

Reflections on feminism, editorial practices and inclusivity through male eyes: what have we learnt? What more can and should we change? *Luis Ignacio Reyes-Galindo; Leandro*

Rodriguez Medina, Universidad de las Americas Puebla

Tapuya is a maturing journal focused on Latin American and Global South STS which was founded by a major feminist philosopher (Harding) and a male Latin American scholar (Rodriguez-Medina). In this talk, the two male members of the 4-member core editorial team will reflect on how working alongside two feminist scholars has provoked changes in our own conceptualization and realization of editorial practices and decisions. While Tapuya in its topic matter is not a feminist journal per se, we believe that our feminist colleagues' perspectives have been determinant in improving journal policies and influential in our own thinking of how to enact 'feminist-compatible' editorial and scholarly work. The talk is also an open call for comments, criticism and advice on how Tapuya may promote further inclusivity and scholarly quality in Latin American scholarship—an ongoing political concern for the editorial team and boards.

Session Organizer:

Olivia Doggett, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

168. Regulating Medical Devices (or Not): Standards, Evidence, and the Political Economy of Medical Device Innovation - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Despite the proliferation of STS scholarship on biomedicalization, pharmaceuticalization, and geneticization, studies interrogating the social construction, regulation, and political economy of medical devices remain slim. Yet, past studies have shown how medical devices and technologies are rich sites for STS investigation. Medical devices are increasingly used in routine clinical care, and include a broad range of objects from MRI machines to assays to surgical implants. Medical devices are regulated in a variety of ways depending on national contexts. In the United States, medical devices, unlike pharmaceuticals, often come to market without rigorous safety and efficacy testing or clinical trials. This regulatory environment purports to encourage innovation, but it also creates uncertainty surrounding potential harm to the public. What regulatory regimes exist in different nations to approve and govern medical devices and innovation? What standards of proof are needed to gain regulatory approval in particular contexts? How do the ways in which medical devices are regulated impact patient care and safety? How does medical device innovation shape scientific knowledge about human bodies, health, and illness? What shapes the political economies of medical device development, adoption, and use? We seek empirical contributions that explore questions about the political economy and regulation of medical technologies and devices, their construction, and the developers who create them. We particularly are interested in papers that examine the implications of emergent medical technologies and devices for inequality and health justice.

Participants:

Medical Device Regulation: The Curious Case of the US FDA
Kelly Joyce, Drexel University; Melanie Jeske, University of California, San Francisco

While the FDA has imposed strict regulation of pharmaceuticals for decades, its oversight of medical devices follows a very different history. And yet, the history of medical device regulation has received little scholarly attention. Medical devices are an unruly category, capturing objects like MRI machines, artificial intelligence tools, and genomic assays, as well as devices that are physically implanted into the body. Recent high profile incidents such as transvaginal mesh and hip implant failures have propelled the regulation of devices into the public eye. In this paper, we offer a sociohistorical analysis of how the United States Food and Drug Administration [US FDA] has come to regulate medical devices, asking critical questions about whose interests this regulatory regime serves, what counts as evidence, and what it means for patient safety. Drawing on analysis of FDA regulation pertaining to medical devices, we identify the social forces that co-constitute the regime of

evaluation for medical technologies. Evaluation of medical devices differs significantly from the one used for pharmaceuticals, and as such provides a provocative site for STS inquiry.

Inscribing Expectations: Medical Assistive Device Design for Imagined Consumers Living in Low-Resource Countries
Vaia Yioula Sigounas, UNC-Chapel Hill

Historically, people living in low-resource countries have managed their mobility problems by modifying donated assistive devices or by designing their own. Recently, however, there has been a drive on the part of the medical devices industry and engineering schools in high-resource settings, such as the United States, to design assistive devices (including prosthetic limbs and wheelchairs) specifically for people living in low-resource settings, such as Uganda. They have been motivated by multiple factors, including the desire to open up less competitive markets for their products, less stringent regulatory requirements for new devices in other countries, and fewer expensive bureaucratic hurdles when these devices become part of the transnational humanitarian aid apparatus. Concurrently, bioengineers designing medical devices for people living in low-resource countries find themselves creating products for people whose wants and needs they often cannot access or do not understand. People living in low-resource countries are not just looking for more affordable devices or ease of repair. Many times, people who have sustained amputation seek devices to solve more than just their mobility problems – they use assistive devices to help them address the negative impact of disability on their identities, social relationships, and finances. Drawing on participant observation and semi-structured interviews with engineers, engineering students, and prosthetic device makers in Uganda and the United States, this paper examines how engineers and assistive device-makers working in the United States project and replicate assumptions about the needs of their end-users as they develop devices intended for recipients living in Uganda.

Regulating Novelty (or Not): The Case of Biomedical Devices and The Double-Bind Problem
Beth Strickland Bloch, University of Kentucky

Every day, in research laboratories across the U.S., biomedical engineers design novel healthcare technologies intended to one day treat patients within clinical settings. The designation of these technologies as “novel” implies that that they are new, or modern, or in some way advanced in their materiality or application. However, not all categories of novel biomedical technologies are subject to the same level of regulatory scrutiny by the Food and Drug Administration (FDA). Innovations classified as devices are less stringently tested than those classified as medicines. This is especially true for certain types of devices, like MRI, prosthetics, and ultrasound, where core system elements are implicitly regarded by designers and regulators as “settled” or “fixed”. This perspective fails to recognize that altered devices, which integrate novel elements (e.g., software, sensors, types of energy) are new themselves new devices. In this paper, the results of interviews with biomedical device engineers are presented in relation to the regulatory politics of novelty. These findings are situated within the recently revitalized STS-theory of Collingridge’s dilemma and the double-bind problem of information and power (Collingridge, 1980; Kudina & Verbeek, 2019). The argument is made to classify altered devices as new devices and to increase their regulatory testing. This approach enables gathering more information about any potentially negative impacts which might result from their use. Biomedical engineers need this information about potential impacts early in the design process since that is when they have the most power to make any necessary changes to the technology.

Regulating Genetics: The Narrowing of Authority over DTC Genetic Health Tests
Hined A Rafeh, Rensselaer Polytechnic

Institute

In 1976, the Medical Device Amendments to the Federal Food, Drug and Cosmetic Act were established; in 2017, the first direct-to-consumer (DTC) genetic health tests were authorized by the FDA under these amendments. This paper analyzes the events that led up to this authorization and how the FDA’s categorization of DTC genetic health tests reveals gaps in the regulation of consumer medical devices. Research on the past two decades on the regulation of DTC genetic health tests shows the shift from a broad debate between multiple stakeholder groups to an extremely narrow regulatory procedure based on the FDA’s specific criteria of determining risk, diagnosis, and health data. To understand this shift, the paper reviews events such as the halted sale of Pathway Genomics DTC genetic tests at Walgreens, the 2010 Congressional hearing of Pathway Genomics, 23andMe and Navigenics, and the FDA’s delivery of warning letters to over 20 genetic companies. My analysis of these events shows how the FDA’s narrow categorization of DTC genetic health tests excludes issues of corporate responsibility, access to genetic data, and the legal distinction of patient/consumer. These issues are exacerbated as private corporations position themselves as “not-health” in response to legislative actions, claiming to provide information but not analysis, service but not healthcare, innovation but not justice. I argue that the gaps in DTC genetic health test legislation reflect the need for legislation that addresses not only genetic data but also for regulating the long-emerging category of digital-health data.

Negotiating the ‘Homebrew’ Loophole: The Regulatory Saga of Laboratory Developed Tests
Melanie Jeske, University of California, San Francisco

In 2010, the US Food and Drug Administration (FDA) announced that it would regulate laboratory developed tests (LDTs). Colloquially referred to as “homebrew” tests, LDTs are defined as in vitro diagnostic tests that are designed, manufactured and used within a single laboratory or healthcare system. In this sense LDTs differ from commercially available test kits, and are often developed in response to unmet needs during local infectious disease outbreaks, rare diseases for which there are often not “markets,” and clinically relevant biomedical research. The category of LDTs itself is quite broad, capturing tests from routine blood assays and those of public health relevance, to complex genomic tests. Noting that the number, type, and complexity of LDTs being offered had greatly increased, and that they were no longer a “mom and pop shop,” the FDA decided it was time to intervene. Upon announcement, the FDA was met with swift resistance from a wide range of stakeholders including public health laboratories, safety-net clinics, commercial and academic laboratories, and biotechnology companies who were concerned regulation would negatively impact patient care and stagnate innovation in diagnostic testing. Some even challenged FDA’s legal authority to regulate LDTs altogether, questioning whether LDTs count as medical “devices.” This paper draws on content analysis of regulatory documents, public meetings, congressional hearings, public comments, and interviews with key actors involved in LDT regulation, offering a critical investigation of the politics at play in diagnostic testing governance.

Session Organizers:

Melanie Jeske, University of California, San Francisco
Kelly Joyce, Drexel University

169. Diseased Landscapes: Health and Illness in Territories of Extraction - I - EMBODIED HARM

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Through the theme of Diseased Landscapes, this panel explores how the nexus of extractivism and political conflict affects environmental and

human health. It aims at bringing together efforts in scholarly practice—including art-based methodologies and activist-oriented research—to historically, politically, and socially situate disease, toxins, pathogens, non-humans, and bodily dysfunction in violent geographies produced by legal and illegal extractivism. We ask how the health conditions of the environment and the body become entangled in places dominated by extractivist economies. What difference does it make to tell stories of armed violence, gendered and racialized dispossession, capitalism, mining, and agrarian expansion through human and more-than-human experiences of health and illness? How are evidence and ignorance about bodies and landscapes produced, used, and abused in contexts marked by extractivist activities? And finally, what practices, methods, and interventions are helpful to establish good relations, capable of disrupting the combined production of disease and violence in old, new, and future territories of extraction?

Participants:

Anatomy of a Tin Rush: Intimate Territories of Skin and Stone

Andrea Marston, Rutgers University, New Brunswick

Porous skins, digestive tracts, and pulmonary tissues trace a precarious border between human bodies and nonhuman natures. Like all geographic borders, this one is more permeable than it appears, and is regularly traversed by materials that are both necessary and harmful to human life. This paper explores the notion of a territorialized body, or a body that comes into socially differentiated existence through practices and processes that draw geological matters into human flesh. Juxtaposing examples of subterranean miners in Bolivia with residents of smoggy urban La Paz, I demonstrate how geological particulates not only traverse bodily boundaries but also contribute to social stratifications that fail to follow clear lines of harm. I argue that the Anthropocene, far from being a strictly planetary affair, is calcified in the very anatomy of differentially exposed communities and individuals, where it is inextricable from locally specific histories and social orders. Such intimate micro-territories of skin and stone, moreover, offer a unique methodological vantage point from which to consider the differentiated unfolding of planetary processes across political and biophysical scales. Understanding the truly human dimensions planetary change, I suggest, is a matter of tracing the particulates of earth caught in the folds of the flesh.

A Tale of Two Glyphosates: The Diseased Landscapes of Gendered and Racialized Dispossession in Colombia *Diana Ojeda, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia; Claudia Rivera; Sonia Serna, Independent researcher*

Geographies of glyphosate use in Colombia have been profoundly shaped both by the Green Revolution and the War on Drugs. While generally presented as two separate glyphosates - one for agricultural use, the other for drug trafficking control-, they rather present a continuum. Informed by feminist political ecology and feminist science and technology studies, this presentation analyzes the diseased landscapes of glyphosate use in the country. Drawing from scholarly, legal and activist work carried out around issues of land access, political violence, environmental defense and reproductive justice in Colombia, we point to the localized and embodied burdens of diseased landscapes in the country. In doing so, we argue that the two glyphosates coalesce in sedimented histories of racialized and gendered dispossession in which the neat boundaries between the direct violence of state fumigations and the ordinary violence of revanchist agrarian policies are erased.

Plotting Harm *Alex Nading*

In the sugarcane plantations of western Nicaragua, environmental health activists are working to confront an epidemic of “chronic kidney disease of non-traditional causes” (CKDnt). Many plantation residents insist that this disease, which was unknown until the 1990s, is related to exposure to toxic pesticides used by plantation companies, but as environmental justice scholars have demonstrated, documenting such exposure is exceedingly

difficult. In this paper, I explore how, amid the mass sickness and death of the CKDnt epidemic, residents circulate stories and digital photographs depicting possible toxic encounters. These constitute an emergent genre of harm. Such stories and photographs spread through word of mouth, spotty mobile phone networks, and other media. This story-circulation is integral to plantation ecology. Residents creatively work within genres of harm to open space for contemplating the role of sugarcane production in shaping the conditions of possible existence—or, health, or well being. The messy process of telling, annotating, and screen sharing, while not globally transmissible as evidence, effectively challenges narrow technoscientific approaches to the environmental ravages of plantation agriculture. This case speaks to the role of “plot” (both the structure of a story and the off-plantation ground of social reproduction) in making toxic worlds thinkable.

Rethinking Landscape In Political Ecologies Of Health: A Case from Ghanaian Gold Mining Country *Heidi Hausermann, Colorado State University*

Since 2008, inherent capitalist crises and instability resulted in high gold prices, leading to proliferation of mining activities worldwide. In Ghana, gold mining has been unregulated and destructive, leading to land grabs, river rerouting, floods, and stagnant water in abandoned pits. These socio-ecological changes have led to critical and compounding health concerns for local people, from increased malaria incidence and “spiritual sicknesses” to food insecurity. Based on a decade of mixed methods research, this paper interrogates how disease dynamics in mining contexts are understood and grappled with in rural communities. I examine the embodied and uneven ways suffering is experienced and detail the relational and more-than-human forms of care that are enacted. Drawing from feminist perspectives, I argue for a more nuanced understanding of landscape in political ecologies of health.

Session Organizer:

Lina Beatriz Pinto-Garcia, Universidad de los Andes

Chair:

Javier Lezaun, University of Oxford

Discussant:

Ann Kelly, King's College London

170. Disempowerment and Empowerment with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems: I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

The relationship between artificial intelligence technology and power is widely discussed, both in the STS community and more broadly. While ethical decision making in the development of AI has been the subject of literally hundreds of frameworks in the past half decade, the consideration of power and AI has been almost entirely absent. The 420,000-member technology professional organization IEEE, through its Standards Association (author of the Ethically Aligned Design report) and its Society on Social Implications of Technology, is developing a discussion of how to prioritize the distribution rather than concentration of power in the development of AI technology. Insights from STS play an important part in examining power and technology. A report in preparation focusses on three aspects, past, present, and future. Past is historical, rediscovering technology's diverse origins, and considering the decolonial. Present draws on legal expertise, the way in which technology currently enforces power. Future is creative, what we could do better. The presentations in this panel each contribute an insight to the issue of power and technology.

Participants:

'Absolute, Measured, Stable' -- and Secret: How Civic Tech Startup Replica Imagines Urban Data *Ben Gansky, Arizona State University*

Urban planning in the United States has for decades flickered between an image of itself as the exercise of technocratic

expertise and as the realization of democratically-determined decisions (Goodman 1971, Clavel 1986). The ‘smart city’ discourse can be read as a means of navigating this tension through the inscription of data-driven planning methods as objective ‘urban science’ (e.g. Clark 2020, Mattem 2013). While urban planners have made use of data-driven techniques since the mid-20th century (Johnson 2020), contemporary big data technics are differentiated not only by their novel constellation of affordances and demands, but by their concentration within firms as opposed to state actors. In the context of smart city planning, these firms rely upon government-produced data while simultaneously laboring to produce public dependence on their services. This paper focuses on the case of Replica, a venture-funded ‘civic tech’ startup spun out of Google-affiliated Sidewalk Labs. My analysis proceeds through my readings of research papers by Replica affiliates, public statements by Replica, and FOIA-ed correspondence between Replica and Portland city planners. I discuss Replica’s epistemological and normative claims in relation to their data and organizational practices. While Replica’s public-facing narrative focuses on its claims to depth of insight, generalizability, objectivity, and privacy-protectiveness, I note the unpublicized but central role of secrecy in their sociotechnical imaginary. In my closing section, I interrogate the limits of what I term Replica’s ‘urban data imaginary’ in the context of their services’ stated use case: support of public planning processes in a democratic society.

A matter of life and death: Social Media, Regimes, and the Global South | The Philippines – a case in point *Lyantoniette Chua, IEEE Global AIS Ethics Initiative, MD4SG, University of the Philippines*

It is not just Maria Ressa’s arrest. Nor Ronnel Mas alone. Digital media is accelerating crackdowns on human rights and basic civil liberties across nations, especially in the Global South. And for the Philippines, the problem on digital deceit: [a] the weaponization of social media, [b] the state-sponsored internet propaganda, [c] the anarchy of numbers within social media algorithms in general, and [d] the lack of accountability among digital platform providers –all together is an imminent fatal flaw for democracy and the lives of many Filipinos. The details on how this is the case, what we can learn from this, what we should and can do are points this paper will shed light on.

From Communication of Science, Technology and Innovation (STI) to Social Appropriation of Science, Technology and Innovation (SASTI) to Intercultural Contexts *Xenia Anaïd Rueda, UNAM; Juan Carlos García Cruz, Cátedras CONACYT/ UAM Xochimilco*

Science and technology are public assets that can and should be used to increase social welfare of people; and solving economic, social, cultural, environmental and preservation of resources at regional, national and global problems. In the present paper it will be described the development and implementation of an intercultural communication model of the Science, Technology and Innovation (STI). This model was implemented in culturally diverse contexts, specifically in indigenous communities in Oaxaca and Chiapas. In addition, there is knowledge generation through social networks of innovation, that includes: a) mechanisms to ensure knowledge will be leveraged socially to meet demands critically analyzed by the different groups involved and by acceptable means from the point of view of those who will benefited; and b) mechanisms and procedures to ensure the participation of those with problems, from conceptualization and formulation to its solution. In this context, the approach of this STI intercultural communication model main purpose is to promote equality of knowledge and multicultural learning by establishing fairer social relations between different communities in the country’s societies and the nation as a whole, especially indigenous communities. Recognition and progressive development of these principles and generally specific cultures

depend on the ability to dialogue and learn from other cultures and knowledge. This requires interaction between community members and specialists from different disciplines in communication processes that preserve and integrate with fairness and rationality the diversity of knowledge in order to expand their cultural horizons through innovative appropriation of external knowledge.

Imaginations Of Transport Automation In Finnish Transport Governance *Janne Olin, Aalto University*

The rapid development of connected and automated vehicles (CAVs) worldwide is bringing along significant uncertainties and urgent questions around societal implications as well as governance of innovation. As public sector actors in transport have historically had an important role in shaping socio-technological trajectories, we need further understanding of localized governance cultures. This study focuses on imaginaries depicted in Finnish transport ministry documents, as the ministry is the most influential pro-automation actor in the Finnish landscape. The document analysis follows the principles of Fairclough’s critical discourse analysis while drawing from Jasanoff’s concept of sociotechnical imaginaries. Document analysis reveals details of pro-automation attitudes, underpinned with expectations for utilizing an important economic opportunity. The preferred path relies on ambitious experimentation and deregulation. While imaginaries such as robot-taxi appear in various documents, no document attempts to distinguish CAV-services specific to Finland. The leadership race is presented as both a question of benefits for forerunners and pride associated with history in telecommunications technologies. This rationalization is underpinned with “winner takes it all” rhetoric stemming from the era of entrepreneur-led Sipilä Cabinet (2015–2019). More recent documents, such as “Transport automation legislation and key policy programme”, reveal an emerging rhetoric about human-centricity of transport automation. In contrast to this rhetoric, there is a dearth of any policies aiming for citizen involvement in the development of transport automation pathways. Overall, the documents depict a one-sided and techno-determinist discourse, where governmental bodies act as mediators of external ideas coming from tech-developers, and the public involvement is almost non-existent.

Session Organizer:

Greg Adamson, IEEE SSIT

171. Displacing Vicious Cycles: Learning Care, Affect and Alternative Politics with Animals, and Other Beings

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Following Karl Polanyi’s thinking, political philosopher James Tully (2018) sees our current global ecosocial crisis as tethered to accelerating “vicious cycles” of earth-degradation under pressures of perpetual capitalist growth. These are cycles of death. In this session, we seek to slow down and find alternate relations and the political engagements they foment, by thinking and discussing some of what we are learning in our research from cycles of life instead. We especially take up inter-being attunement and affective relations with animals, plants, lands, waters – some of us guided and enriched by our decolonial engagements with / as Indigenous Peoples in their animal, land and water relations; some of us involved in ethological, biological, and ethnographic engagement directly with various living beings and entities – and how being captured by them aids in shifting our attention and actions to livability, mutual care, and toward Tully’s alternative and resurgent politics sourced in “virtuous cycles”. Our interlocutors include, among others: eels (Mi’kmaq: Kataq), ducks (Anatids), ravens (Corvids), whales (Cetaceans), wolves (Canids), medicinal plants, and living Land, Air, and Water forms.

Participants:

Embodied listening with whales *Amy Donovan, McGill University*

Whales’ existence and ways of existing are under constant threat

from anthropogenic pollution and noise in the ocean. Recent work in marine biology has demonstrated the richness of whales' social and communicative lives, and their capacity for empathy. This paper takes up the question of who whales are, that is, their own affective relations with one another and their surroundings, by way of an embodied listening practice. Listening, as marine biologists do, to recordings of whales proposes a vibratory anthropology, tuned to the echolocations of whales and rendering them audible by the bodies of human interlocutors through sensory, textured storytelling. I interweave the findings of such a practice with preliminary discussion of ethnographic interview data, exploring what can be felt and articulated through anthropological attunement to the relational encounters of marine biologists in the field with whales.

On Etuaptmumk & Netukulimk: Notes on their proper practice, from a Mi'kmaw eel harvester *Aaron Prosper, U. PEI, Dalhousie U.*

In recent years there has been a growing popularity to incorporate Indigenous knowledge systems and research methodologies into present-day Western academic research. This is especially prominent in Western academic research projects conducted with, in, or near Indigenous communities. This paradigm shift has been influenced, in large part, by a number of significant academic research policy changes, for example TCPS2 chapter 9. However, there remains a significant lack of understanding around how these knowledge systems might truly be applied within current Western academic research protocols and processes. This paper will explore how the growing movement to 'Indigenize' Western academic research can serve to only further misuse, co-opt, and romanticize Indigenous knowledge systems. Specific commentary will be given to the ways in which the Mi'kmaw concept of Etuaptmumk, or Two-Eyed Seeing, has been misused, co-opted, and romanticized in present-day Western academia. Lastly, this paper will explore how the Mi'kmaw harvesting practice of Netukulimk (a Mi'kmaw harvesting philosophy) informs Mi'kmaw environmental, ecological, treaty, and community relations. And how Mi'kmaw communities conceptualize Netukulimk through a Two-Eyed Seeing framework, often removed from Western academia, to promote community health and wellness. This perspective will be provided through my personal experience as a young Mi'kmaw eel harvester from Eskasoni First Nation, and how Netukulimk informs my personal relations with local environment, ecologies, treaties, and my community.

Affective sciences, domestication and the inevitable bond. *Simon Gadbois, Psychology & Neuroscience, Dalhousie University; Tessa Cosman, Psychology & Neuroscience, Dalhousie University*

The association and domestication of animals may have had an unintended consequence: to paraphrase Davis and Balfour (1992), an "inevitable bond". We will examine the shared affective space between early humans and wolves, and the likely evolution of the bond over centuries until the advent of farming, when, most likely, the relationship between canids and humans may have become more "planned" (via selective breeding) to broaden the utilitarian aspect of the relationship. First, we will discuss the possible genesis of the process in the early human-animal association, more specifically with the Human - Wolf - Raven triad. Second, we will discuss the contributions of ethology, psychology and neuroscience in defining the (inevitable) affective bond between humanity and our non-human counterparts, and examine the gap between modern affective sciences, the paradoxical and complex relationship humans maintained with many domesticated species, and the (implicit?) knowledge of many cultures on the targeted phenotypes to facilitate the bond. The often dismissed affective life of animals in relation to imprinting in modern behavioural sciences and neurosciences will be presented. We suggest that an affective

(not cognitive) reframing of the sciences of animal attachment is needed to advance our understanding of the complexity and richness of the human-animal bond.

Accepting Raven's Invitation: On Personal, Political and Cosmopolitical Relations *Brian Noble, Dalhousie University*

In 2009, while visiting the University of Victoria in unsundered Lekwungen territories, I had a profoundly affective experience: that of being gifted a raven feather — literally by a raven, *Corvus corax*, who invited me to accept the feather. After recounting this poignant interaction, I will slow down and consider how I have come to terms with the layered up consequences of the event, and of my having accepted the raven's invitation. I will consider the affective, cognitive, and perhaps most importantly, the political consequences — or to use Stenger's proposition the cosmopolitical consequences — of our interchange and the potential obligations of mutual care flowing from this. I want then to consider such "personal" invitations from animals or other non-humans also as political ones for us to embrace as engaged STS scholars, to join in political exchange between species as collectives - polities of collective affect — and how this resonates deeply with political relations often sought by Indigenous Peoples. Part of my inspiration is having witnessed how many Indigenous Peoples I have been honoured to partner with, already engage in such political "compacts" with animal and other non-human collectives - in their embodied and enshadowed manifestations — whether in alliance, in kinship, in treaty. A second part of my inspiration is in considering that which may hold scientific and social scientific praxis back from such possibilities; or alternatively whether and how we are undergoing a transformative shift to the relational, affective and political, as part of the etho-ecological demand of our current moment.

Composing with Plants; Discerning their Call *Julie Laplante, Department Of Sociology And Anthropology, University Of Ottawa*

Wandering in the ancestral forest of Bassinglègè with a Bantu healer in Cameroon, he lets plants attract his attention to discern how to heal someone who had earlier sought his guidance. Thinking with plants, other living materialities, human and not, is his vocation or his calling. A calling, as in calling with, called by, calling as if the world mattered, can be further understood as an affective relation leading us on a particular path, in this case one inspired by what the world has to tell or how it manifests its presence. This filial sentiment of belonging and surrender can be contrasted with most of today's ways of doing science in which the researcher holds himself in front of the world or of "nature" as before a foreign, indefinable object. I want to explore the former position as it enables to understand what healers do, as well as what scientists could do more, especially anthropologists. Anchoring my thoughts in fieldwork done with healers in Africa, Java and Brazilian Amazonia, I want to express ways in which plants can both augment or diminish our desire and effort to persevere in existence. I'm thus interested in the that which inheres or subsists in our flesh and imagination, making the vegetal become human or cosmological.

Session Organizers:

Brian Noble, Dalhousie University
Amy Donovan, McGill University

Chairs:

Brian Noble, Dalhousie University
Amy Donovan, McGill University

172. Politics of the Future: Theoretical Approaches in STS

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

The concept of the future is re-emerging as an urgent topic on the academic agenda. Sociological interest in the future as a dimension of action in the present goes back to the Schutz, Mead and others, but recently,

perspectives from Science and Technology Studies and governmentality studies have come to dominate. In these perspectives, we identify two rough approaches, a) the study of promissory/normative visions, and b) the study of 'futures-in-the-making' and correlated styles of anticipation. In this panel, we aim to connect those two approaches by focusing on the 'politics of the future': the social processes and practices that allow particular imagined futures to become socially performative. In doing so, we have three aims: (1) identify the leading social-theoretical work on the future; (2) conceptualise the relationship of the imagination of the future with social practices and the performance of reality; (3) discuss various theoretical frameworks explaining how images of the future become performative. Specifically, we explore whether these new concepts such as 'techniques of futuring' can meaningfully add to the gamut of concepts around the materiality of future-making, the politics of anticipation, and the sociotechnical imaginaries that shape sociotechnical futures.

Participants:

Techniques of Futuring: How Imagined Futures become Persuasive *Jeroen Oomen, University of Utrecht; Jesse Hoffman, Urban Futures Studio / Utrecht University; Maarten Hajer, Utrecht University*

In this presentation, we focus on the 'politics of the future': the social processes and practices that allow particular imagined futures to become socially performative. Acknowledging that the performativity of such imagined futures is well-understood, we argue that how particular visions come about and why they become performative is underexplained. By focusing on imagined futures not only as 'futures-in-the-making' (as work on the politics of anticipation might) but also the dramaturgical and discursive practices of 'futures-as-immersive-performance', we aim to develop a performative understanding of futuring – proposing a dramaturgical analysis to investigate how actors actively 'bring the future into the present' through performances using particular narratives, settings and configurations. To do so, we rely on the 'techniques of futuring' concept, defined as 'practices bringing together actors around one or more imagined futures and through which actors come to share particular orientations for action' (Hajer & Pelzer, 2018: 222). To further our understanding of how such practice bring people together around particular imagined futures, we introduce the concept of 'dramaturgical regime' as well as a dramaturgical framework. In short, this presentation discusses a theoretical framework to explain how images of the future gain performative traction, in conversation with existing approaches based on performative visions and 'futures-in-the-making'.

What are futures made of and by? *Christopher Groves, Cardiff University, Cardiff, Wales, United Kingdom*

Theoretical approaches to 'the future' in STS oscillate between two positions. On the one hand, we have the study of promissory visions (as in the sociology of expectations) and on the other, the study of knowledge practices (conceptualised as styles of anticipation). The first foregrounds the role of representations, how they circulate and act as intermediaries in the formation of networks. The second foregrounds the role of practices, comprising material components (technologies, infrastructures), competences and meanings. Both these perspectives enrich the understanding of how futures — imagined and represented, intended and enacted, but also implicit and presaged — capture representational and non-representational aspects of future-orientation in the present. They have also furthered the study of the performative effects of futures in the present in terms of (co-)producing social orders. At the same time, these approaches have to some extent overlooked how the future 'becomes a problem' that can be solved in and across different social contexts and at different times. Specifically, we lack analytical tools to understand how representations and practices themselves exhibit particular discernible patterns of future orientation over time, and how these patterns reproduce particular forms of subjectivity. To explore what these might be, I stage a dialogue

between the concept of future horizons (Adam and Groves 2007, Groves 2017), understood as diagrams (Foucault) or 'maps of destiny' (Deleuze) for assemblages of practices and representations, and the dramaturgical understanding of 'techniques of futuring' outlined by Oomen, Hoffman and Hajer (2021).

The politics of future-making in Transformations towards Sustainability *silke beck, UFZ Leipzig*

This paper uses the conceptual socio-technical imaginaries (STI) framework (Jasanoff and Kim, 2015) to expose crucial but neglected governance issues in sustainability transformations. Drawing upon a review of the expanding literature in the field of transition and transformation studies, the paper outlines how imaginaries project visions of sustainable futures and hereby constitute or justify certain policy trajectories. Explicitly addressing the political and normative dimensions of future-making, I illustrate how STI research helps uncover taken-for-granted assumptions that often shut down resistant imaginings and helps to make visible alternate pathways. Reconstructing the emergence of negative emission technologies, I show how STIs help us to understand how visions of a sustainable future can legitimate cognitive path-dependencies and material/discursive lock-ins, reinforcing power structures and resource-intensive lifestyles. The STI lens allows us to explore why specific technical solutions (such as carbon removal technologies) have emerged as privileged options to address global environmental problems. Explicitly addressing the ways in which understandings of transformation are co-produced with the structures and practices that (seek to) drive them, an STI approach shows how not only transformations are political, but how the shaping of knowledges and imagined futures about them is too. While the STI concept helps us to understand futures in the making, however, the public enactment and performativity of STIs are topics that call for more attention and a broader engagement with corresponding approaches in STS/ sociology of the future. In this paper, I will address this broader engagement and what can be learned from alternative approaches.

Imagining and Performing No Futures *Richard Tutton, University of York*

Sociologists have developed and employed a range of analytical strategies to examine how futures are made and contested, utilising representational, performative and materialist frameworks. But with growing interest in the concept of the future, there is a need to consider the relationship between the 'politics of the future' and power relations: whose futures are imagined, debated, contested, and for whom are futures (to paraphrase Arjun Appadurai) nightmares, doubts, or shrinking possibilities? Additionally, who does the imagining of such futures, how, where, and why? This paper adds to the repertoire of sociological research on the imagination of the future and its relationship to social practices by considering how scholars have made claims about how states of no future – or conditions of futurelessness – are produced as an effect of societal, political and technological processes. Through examining work in different disciplinary clusters, I explore how these images of no futures become socially performative and how they engage with questions of political power and technoscience. In doing so, I shed light not only on how desirable futures become socially persuasive, but also how conditions of futurelessness become persuasive.

Session Organizer:

Jeroen Oomen, University of Utrecht

Chair:

Maarten Hajer, Utrecht University

173. A Good Life, In Theory: Thinking and Living with Climate Change - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

In recent years, an increasing amount of STS and STS-aligned scholarship has used provocative and conceptually creative ways to address the exceptional challenges posed by global climate change. A number of theoretical orientations have emerged within Anthropocene studies, such as new materialism and Gaia-based approaches, offering sophisticated ways for scholars to think through the implications of climate change for both human and more-than-human life. However, these shifts have also inspired backlash from those who argue that the constant search for new theory obfuscates empirical realities and the politics of responsibility. Particularly in light of the climate crisis, the at-times tenuous and overlapping relationships between theoretical creativity, empirical rigor, and everyday action demand renewed critical attention. This panel seeks to critically engage these fragile relationships within Anthropocene STS scholarship to illuminate potentials for individual, academic, and political meaning in a warming world. How can scholars hold onto both climate realism and creative conceptualizations of more-than-humans? Does the urgency of global warming demand a more overt level of political engagement in academia? Can we effectively reconcile the conceptual utility of our theoretical methodologies with the pragmatic and embodied risks of ecological justice? Papers will address these multiscalar gaps, reframing potential discrepancies as constructive spaces of possibility for good relations between fellow earthlings. Session I, "Circular Imaginaries," features theoretical pathways for situating boundedness, temporality, and subjectivity in the Anthropocene. Papers drawing on land art, critical theory, market-based ecology, and AI climate modeling suggest new understandings of linearity, circularity, and individuation within discourses of growth, decay, and renewal in climate change scholarship.

Participants:

Geomorphic Aesthetics and Thermodynamic Imagination:
Reading "Spiral Jetty" in the Anthropocene *benek cincik, The University of Edinburgh*

In April 1970, Robert Smithson poured six thousand five hundred tons of basalt rocks and earth over a period of three weeks to construct his four hundred and sixty meters long and four and a half meters wide, twice coiling enigmatic Spiral Jetty (hereafter SJ) at the Rozel Point in the Great Salt Lake in Utah. In this paper, I will investigate how the decentering of human alludes to the dissolution of anthropocentric notions of subjectivity, through focusing on SJ's relationship with entropy and Smithson's thermodynamic imagination. The entropic nexus between sun, heat, and salt crystals forms the conceptual and material spine of the SJ project. By focusing on this entropic nexus, I will analyze the SJ earthwork's positioning within a larger spatiotemporal frame and reflect on its engagement with planetary change. I will explore how the SJ project problematizes the notion of the end through positing the differentiation of 'geologic life' along with the material dedifferentiation processes of the desert and thereby converting itself into a future fossil. Within this prism, I will relate Smithson's concept of "abstract geology" which recasts human thought within geo-logics and specifically the SJ film's crystal sequence where he points at his own dissolution "into a unicellular beginning" with philosopher Gilbert Simondon's notion of the crystal as the exemplar of the processes of individuation. While the SJ earthwork is marooned in salt crystals accompanied with archae that might endure long after the humans are gone, the SJ poses a processual, non-anthropocentric, and "telescoped" view of an end that is translated by chronogenesis.

The Circular Economy as a good life A new way to address climate change or an eco-modernist political project?

Vincenzo Pavone, Consejo Superior Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC); Mario Pansera, Bristol University

The notion of Circular Economy (CE) has recently gained traction, replacing sustainable development and acting as an umbrella term to assemble policy proposals addressing climate change but drawing from different socio-technical imaginaries such as eco-innovation, green growth or the new green deal. The

CE is often defined as an economic system of closed loops in which raw materials, components and products lose their value as little as possible, renewable energy sources are used and systems thinking is at the core (Kohronen, et al. 2018). Reconciling economic growth with the goal of reverting climate change, the CE promises to be the long awaited solution to the current capitalist crisis. Drawing from works done on the bioeconomy (Goven and Pavone 2015), we argue that the CE should rather be understood as an eco-modernist political project stimulating the self-regulation of industry and transferring responsibilities from the state to the market (Mol & Spaargaren, 2000). Through market-based instruments, such as environmental taxes, and technological changes, the CE promotes a process of 'economizing ecology', attributing economic value to environmental resources and burdens, promoting techno-fixes and justifying institutional changes to facilitate them (Lewidow and Rahman 2020). As a result of an analysis of several EU and national policy documents, this paper argues that the CE aims at projecting the illusion of radical change while concealing that the envisioned technological developments strive to maintain the status quo, endorsing a specific vision of good life and displacing alternatives such as eco-localization or conviviality (Genovese & Pansera, 2020).

Thinking 'Limits' and its 'Translations' with Michel Serres – A Critical Perspective on Limitarisms in Political Ecology
Lilian Kroth, The University of Cambridge

The conceptualization of 'limits' have been decisive for the research around climate change, the distribution and exploitation of resources and apocalyptic end-of-world-scenarios, especially since the 1970s onwards. The 'limits of growth', as promoted by the Club of Rome, or more recently 'planetary boundaries' have had crucial impact on political rhetorics in regard to human's relationship with the environment. This paper attempts to critically engage with the notions of the 'limit' and its potential to successfully translate for world-narratives in the realm of political ecology. For this, I will draw attention to the work of Michel Serres and the way he conceives 'limits' and 'boundaries' in its conceptual differences, as well as in its role to 'translate' between the history and philosophy of science, mathematics, aesthetics, and politics. To exemplify Serres' methodological approach to a structural analysis of limits, I will take passages Hermes, Geometry, Rome, The Birth of Physics, Atlas and Hominescence into account. Serres's insightful contribution to think 'limits' and 'boundaries' in a necessarily transdisciplinary way resonates with contemporary critical voices in the 'limits'-discourse in political ecology (Bühlmann/Hovestadt/Michael; Kallis; Garforth; Demos et al), in regard to which this paper tries to stress the critical contribution Serres gains especially from historical and philosophical examination.

Times of Knowledge, Climate and Artificial Intelligence
Govert Valkenburg, NTNU

Climate change and climate science have particular time perspectives. Climate change happens at many different time scales, ranging from short and urgent to long and almost unnoticeable. Climate science is mostly tied to mathematical, linear conceptions of time, that needs to accommodate these short and long time frames. If artificial intelligence (AI) is to help make sense of the climate system and climate change, it is most likely tied to those mathematical, linear conceptions. But how enabling or constraining is this, given that human thinking has produced a wealth of notions of time across ages and cultures? Since climate change is a complex, sociotechnical (or socio-scientific if you like) problem, facing it requires a broad range of knowledges. If AI reinforces the dominance of a narrow conception of time, then its computing power may in fact come at the cost of losing diversity of knowledges that can be mobilized to confront climate change. In this presentation, I discuss the notions of time that circulate in both AI and climate science, and explore how these are limiting, compared to other

notions of time. The discrepancy has important consequences for the knowledge that gets to speak to the decisions we make. Knowledges connected to mathematical, linear time frames are likely to have a bigger voice than knowledges that are farther detached from those. If technology is “politics by other means”, then AI is knowledge politics by time-specific means. Underlying notions of time are crucial to understanding these politics.

Session Organizer:

Claire Oliver, Department of History and Philosophy of Science, University of Cambridge

Chair:

Claire Oliver, Department of History and Philosophy of Science, University of Cambridge

174. Designing and Distributing Food Practices and Knowledges

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

This panel curates a conversation among scholars who research food production and delivery practices in STS. How do digital technologies merge the production and consumption of food? How does academic research travel and not travel, translate and mistranslate into food policy? How has Uber during the COVID-19 pandemic shaped food delivery in urban centers? As a whole this panel considers the ways technologies and scientific studies make and remake food distribution in urban centers?

Participants:

Digital fooding, cashless marketplaces and reconnection in intermediated third places: Conceptualizing metropolitan food provision in the age of prosumption *Raphaël Stephens, UMR LISIS - Université Gustave Eiffel; Marc Barbier, Institut National de la Recherche Agronomique*

This article adopts the concept of prosumption in order to better understand the array of contemporary food sustainability transition initiatives that often come under the umbrella term of Alternative Food Networks (AFNs). AFNs have developed in parallel to prosumption, which is significant because AFNs are oriented towards localized and direct relationships between producers and consumers, while prosumption explains the hybridization of the consumer into a more complex and productive actor. Scholars argue that producer-consumer reconstructions enable greater transparency and information exchange between the two types of actors. In addition, digitalization has recently brought new perspectives for both prosumption and AFN research. We explain the digital food prosumption phenomenon by drawing upon several years of research on an alternative food network with strong digital focus – La Ruche qui dit Oui!. As a decentralized network of local food operations that converge around a digital platform, it provides innovative virtual-material mediations between producers and consumers. This suggests that increasingly, consumers may be getting more deeply engaged in the (co-)production of commodities across different sectors and activities. Thus, while the prosumption and AFN literatures have mostly existed in parallel, future efforts should be made to intersect these two areas of sociological research. This is particularly pertinent today, as both prosumption and AFN phenomena are now increasingly mediated by powerful digital technologies. In the digital age, the alternative food prosumer phenomenon may well contribute to reconfiguring global food flows and industrial cultures towards sustainability.

The Governance Predicament in Technology Policy:

Reflections from Systematic Review of Ractopamine Literature *Ying-Kai Liao, National Taiwan Normal University; Shiang-Yao Liu, National Taiwan Normal University*

In the second half of 2020, due to the decision of Taiwan’s government to open up imports of pork containing ractopamine

from the USA, a series of debates about health, ecology, and livestock production have emerged in Taiwan’s society. It becomes necessary to understand how the academic research results regarding ractopamine have been quoted and interpreted as the basis for discussion of topics. In this systematic review of literature, we designed a coding scheme for judging the positive and negative effects on health and ecology reported in the academic papers. A total of 511 articles were found in the SCOPUS database since 2000 to present. The coding scheme was also used to analyze documents both from government that support imports and the major advocacy groups that hold an anti-import stance. Results of the literature review indicated that human health and ecological concerns are not the focus of mainstream academia. The academic research that has a significant impact on policy-making or risk management is not easy to appear in policy debates. Analysis of documents further showed that both the government and advocacy groups selectively quoted a small amount of unilateral academic literature. The way they quoted academic papers reveals their misunderstanding of scientific significance in research and overinterpretation of research results. According to the results, we suggest that for any controversial and risk-related technology policies, or in the early stage of policy discussion, a large-scale academic literature review could be implemented by a third-party organization in order to achieve transparent governance.

Food design during the pandemic: has the crisis brought us a critical opportunity or hegemonic condemnation? *Ligia Afreixo, Universidade de Aveiro; Catarina Ribeiro, Universidade de Coimbra; Francisco Providencia, Universidade de Aveiro*

Eating is an act that surpasses the survival regime to become an act of sharing, meeting and identity. Eating is an exchange action, not only of flavours and recipes but also of services. When we eat something made outside the home, whether on the road or through a take-away system, we are not only enjoying a service but also giving meaning to what we eat, space and the people who make it possible. In the pandemic of COVID-19, food’s social and community attitude was interrupted, and the park of small and medium-sized traditional restaurants. This communication intends to present and analyze the most significant impacts of the Portuguese urban society’s food culture (study developed by observation in the metropolitan area of Porto). Based on the analysis of meal delivery platforms such as Uber eats and Glovo, there is a framework of intentions for food consumption structured in two vectors: the industrial massification of food multinationals and greater openness to food’s cultural diversity origins, with particular focus on eastern supply. It recognizes the quality of its regional food as one of the main factors of tourist notability in Porto’s area, in a vast profusion of traditional restaurants, now closed by sanitary impositions but without the capacity to digitally re-adapt. We recognize that this environment of the obligatory enclosure is not only not; it seems to have brought a more excellent social reflection on food and contributed to an evident loss of cultural differentiation.

Session Organizer:

Raphaël Stephens, UMR LISIS - Université Gustave Eiffel

175. Epistemic Infrastructures - II

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Participants:

Epidemiological Maps As Epistemic Infrastructure In The Governance Of Cancer In Africa *David Reubi, Kings College London; Thandeka Cochrane, King’s College London*

This paper looks at cancer maps as a core ‘epistemic infrastructure’ that is produced by and constitutive of the epidemiological surveillance of malignancy in Africa. Through

the comparison of an early cancer mapping project for Burkitt's Lymphoma in the 1960s and the contemporary cancer maps produced by IARC, the paper unpacks how the epistemic infrastructure of maps has shifted from research and exploration to policy and governance over the last half century. In focusing on maps, we ask how maps function as a particular aesthetic of quantification. Maps are a key technologies in public health for visualizing disease and locating it in space and time (see Koch 2005, 2011). As modalities of quantification maps serve as instruments of governance, power and coloniality (see Choudhry 2016; Jeremy 2000; Shore and Wright 2015). But what do maps help us see and what do they occlude? Maps draw lines across the world, creating invisible markers and divisions, they represent and fixate territories and turn terrains into symbols and numbers, and they bring into being new kind of people and tell stories about the world while erasing and silencing others (Reubi 2020). Through the example of the maps for Burkitt's Lymphoma, we show how cancer mapping in the 1960s was focused on questions research, aetiology, and possibly even cure. The later maps of IARC shifted away from a focus on research and aetiology, towards an emphasis on government and global health policy. In this we trace how maps shifted from being technologies for 'knowing Africa' to technologies for 'managing Africa'.

From rankings to plural mappings of science for Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) *Ismael Rafols, Centre for Science & Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University; Ed Noyons, CWTS, Leiden University; Hugo Confraria, UECE, ISEG, University of Lisboa; Tommaso Ciarli*

Responding to policy demands, a flurry of information analysts from corporations such as Elsevier, think-thanks such as NESTA, or universities such as ours are rapidly developing methods to establish how research is contributing to SDGs through mapping publications. The assumption is that publications can univocally be qualified as either being related or unrelated to SDGs – thus allowing comparison and ranking between research projects or organisations according to the amount of publications on a given SDG. In a new study we have found a high degree of inconsistency obtained through different approaches, as recently reported by Armitage et al., (2020). We propose that these inconsistencies represent different interpretations of SDGs: there is no a single objective 'truth' about which research is relevant for reaching SDGs. Given the variety of understandings regarding the relationship between research and SDGs, we warn against one single, preferred or consensus way of mapping SDGs to publications, since such mapping would be likely to reproduce hegemonic perspectives on SDGs – often given by rich countries at influential institutional actors. However, we propose that alternative quantification approaches can be developed in ways that foster pluralistic understandings of science and SDGs. Since different stakeholders have contrasting and often conflicting views about the relationships between science and SDGs, we develop an interactive platform that allows stakeholders to explore in a global map of science publications potentially relevant for SDGs in a plural and conditional way.

<https://public.tableau.com/profile/ed.noyons#!/vizhome/UKStrin gsSDGtocommunities/Dashboard1>

Climate Science In Numbers: Carbon Governance, Mathematical Relations And Transitions Targets *Francesco Colona, Department of Thematic Studies - Technology and Social Change, Linköping University*

Like many arenas of science-policy interface, carbon governance is shaped by quantification processes. Here numbers are often finite quantities and – in mathematical jargon – absolute values. Their aim is to influence policy by numerically describing more or less sustainable alternative futures. For instance, the 2018 policy summary of the report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change stresses the importance of keeping global

warming below 1.5 degree centigrade compared to pre-industrial levels, assuming it as an absolute and specific measure of success in avoiding irreversible and catastrophic climatic change.

Similarly, the effectiveness of Carbon Capture and Storage technologies is often measured by the absolute number of kilotons of carbon that they are able to capture and permanently keep from the atmosphere. In contrast, ClimateView, a Swedish company providing software services to plan and visualize the shifts necessary to address the climate crisis, suggests that numbers in carbon governance practices are effective and relevant only as they enact relations – not absolute values – between carbon indicators, or between hypothesized carbon emissions and specific policies. Based on document analysis and interviews with climate scientists, policy makers and software engineers, this paper intervene in recent STS debates on quantification and numbers and show how climate adaptation policymaking is facilitated by approaching numbers as tools that are primarily capable of establishing relations.

"If We Build It, They Will Come": Emerging Epistemic Infrastructures in The Case of SDG 1 *Justyna Bandola-Gill, University of Edinburgh*

Ending poverty is the first objective outlined in the SDGs – and for the first time this includes multidimensional poverty. The introduction of the new concept of poverty prompted a rapidly growing epistemic infrastructure, connecting actors, institutions and data. Unlike the predominant literature focusing on existing infrastructures, this paper explores the emergence of new statistical systems and the contestations around them. In particular, through interviews with key actors in International Organisations and their field offices in developing countries, it will explore how new policy concepts – such as multidimensional poverty – are problematised, instrumentalised and institutionalised in global public policy.

Decolonizing Global Health: The Global Health Security Index And Its Casualties of Preparedness *Manjari Mahajan, New School University*

The 2019 Global Health Security Index assessed the United States and the United Kingdom as the two countries best prepared to address a catastrophic pandemic. The preparedness rankings of this index have had little correlation with the actual experiences of COVID-19 in various countries. In explaining this discrepancy, the paper argues that better indicators and more data would not have fixed the problem. Rather, the prevailing paradigm of global health security that informs instruments such as the Global Health Security Index needs to be interrogated. This dominant paradigm narrowly conceptualizes global health security in terms of the availability of a technical infrastructure to detect emerging infectious diseases and prevent their contagion, but profoundly undertheorises the broader social and political determinants of public health. The neglect of social and political features is amplified in instruments such as the Global Health Security Index that privilege universalized templates presumed to apply across countries but that prove to be inadequate in assessing how individual societies draw on their unique histories to craft public health responses.

Session Organizer:

Marlee Tichenor, University of Edinburgh

Chair:

Sotiria Grek, The University of Edinburgh

176. 1. Socioecological Resilience and Governance of Agri-food Systems

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

The rise of sustainability sciences followed the signing of the three Rio conventions (CBD, UNCCD and GCC). Consequently, the last two decades of the 20th century saw the rise from multidisciplinary to inter and transdisciplinary research dealing with complex systems. Most

conservationists ended up accepting that notions of pristine environments have not helped but hindered conservation efforts. Sustainability studies corroborated that the conventional distinction of ecosystems and social systems had made it more difficult to understand socio-ecological interactions. At the same time STS revealed the failure of attempting to increase agro-food resilience capacities through technological means alone. However, reforms have been uneven not only across the developed and developing world but also across sectors. Worryingly in no other sector have the problems been more acute and the resistance to change more decisive than in agriculture. Agriculture continues to be the main driver of deforestation and habitat loss (WWF 2020). It contributes a significant share of the greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions -17% through agricultural activities and 7-14% through changes in land use (Howden et al. 2007; OECD 2020). And although the STS critique of the political use of “desertification” discourse, there is agreement that agriculture continues to be a main driver of soil depletion and erosion. Therefore, it is urgent to identify the barriers and incentives, facilitating or hindering to transitioning towards sustainable agri-food systems. Presentations of this session would critically examine case studies with view to strengthen collaborative research in this area.

Participants:

Controversy over livestock and pasture restoration in Brazil:

The limitations of proposed transitions *Thais Rozas Teixeira, Universidade de Brasilia - UnB*

According to FAO, by 2050 the meat production across the globe will double, encouraged by the growing population and the increasing demand for animal products, especially meat. In this context, Brazil, with the second large herd in the world, is the largest beef exporter. However, livestock production has a large responsibility for its greenhouse gas emissions, especially considering methane from enteric fermentation of ruminants and carbon from degraded pastures. That’s why the country’s emissions are peculiar because most of them are not derived from fossil fuel combustion but from land-use changes and farming. Although livestock is a nationally relevant economic activity, it’s also one of the largest contributors to climate change, and that’s why Brazil’s international commitments to the UNFCCC include, among other practices and technologies, the restoration of 15 million hectares of degraded pastures. This technology is related to the politics adopted nationally to achieve the commitments by increasing soil capacity to sequester carbon on these restored pastures. Our aim was to investigate how scientific knowledge about soil sequester potential is made, understanding this as a socio-technical controversy in the context of transitions towards sustainable agri-food systems. Therefore, this paper can contribute to the understanding of how this mitigation practice appears in a variety of strategies for a low carbon society, including livestock production. Moreover, we will argue that, although scientists disagree about the mitigation potential of restored pastures, both pathways are linked to resistance to these possible transitions, maintaining the same systems of animal production and consumption.

EcoSol-agroecology networks respond to the Covid-19 crisis in Brazil’s Baixada Santista region *Les Levidow, Open University*

The concept of ‘social-ecological resilience’ has been defined in various ways, e.g. as ‘the capacity to adapt or transform in the face of change in social-ecological systems, particularly unexpected change, in ways that continue to support human well-being’ (Chapin et al., 2009). This emphasises a transformative potential in production-consumption systems, such as food relocalisation conserving and recycling natural resources, while also enhancing community cohesion and well-being. Such an agenda can be illustrated by the agroecology-based solidarity economy in Latin America or EcoSol-agroecology for short. For at least the past decade, these solidarity networks built collective capacities for self-managing short food-supply chains (circuitos curtos). Agroecological producers built closer relationships with

consumers whose purchases support environmentally sustainable cultivation methods. These solidaristic markets have built new socio-cultural identities through cooperative efforts by small-scale producers, civil society groups and local authorities. From early 2020 onwards, however, the Covid-19 crisis imposed extra hygiene requirements, which aggravated the previous difficulties of declining Federal support. Nevertheless some EcoSol-agroecology initiatives found new opportunities to expand circuitos curtos, as in Brazil’s Baixada Santista coastal region. In several towns there, creative adaptations made the initiatives more visible, maintained consumer trust, expanded food sales and contributed to donations, framed as solidarity rather than charity. The expansion built on prior collective capacities of mainly women’s cooperatives linked with local solidarity groups, sometimes with support from the municipality. A region-wide solidarity network organised a regular multi-actor knowledge-exchange process, helping to build proximities of various kinds. In all those ways, EcoSol-agroecology networks exemplify moves towards social-ecological resilience.

Socioecological resilience assessment as basis to reach consensus regarding innovation paths in the agricultural sector *OSCAR A. FORERO, AGROSAVIA*

In Colombia SNIA, the law 1876 of 2017 provided a legal framework for the development of the National System of Science and Technology in the Agricultural sector. The law instructs creation of territorial innovation systems at Municipal and Departmental levels. A main goal of SNIA is to facilitate transitioning from providing technical advice to stakeholders to enable comprehensive rural extension service. The legislators aimed to address STS critique indicating that increasing sustainability of agrifood systems would be likely to be attained only or mainly through technological adoption. Agrosavia, the largest research centre in the agricultural sector in Colombia, developed a methodology to strengthen or creating territorial innovation systems by facilitating stakeholders to evaluate their socio-ecological resilience capacities; for the agreeing on innovations paths to be pursued. This paper examines the experiences of piloting the methodology in three distinctive biogeographical areas of Colombia. The systematization efforts of the process are summarised and a critique of the methodology and of the process of implementation is presented with aim to identify barriers and incentives that encourage or prevent increasing resilient capacities of stakeholders regarding agri-food systems.

The Lock-in Patterns in Transitioning Towards Sustainable Agri-food Systems for the Cattle Production of the Colombian Orinoquia and the Urban Area of Bogota. *Xavier Fargetton, Agrosavia; OSCAR A. FORERO, AGROSAVIA*

Colombian Orinoquia region is a key element of the foodshed of the urban area of Bogota and its 8 million inhabitants. The cattle producers of Orinoquia supply over 60% of the red meat for Bogota’s consumers. Orinoquia cattle sector includes more than 40,000 farms, produces 1 million head of cattle per year, and uses 10 million hectares of land of which a significant part is not considered adequate for cattle production from an ecosystem service point of view. Over the last 20 years, all the initiatives of transitioning towards a more sustainable system have remarkably failed. Between 2017 and 2020, we researched the upstream, midstream and downstream links of the red meat agri-food system of Orinoquia-Bogota region. We identified severe lock-in patterns of cultural, social, technical, economic, and environmental natures which create several critical bottlenecks along the entire value chain. The two conceptual frameworks of complex systems and coexistence of socioeconomic agricultural systems show promising results at identifying the structures underlying the red meat agri-food system of the Orinoquia-Bogota region and at unveiling new options for transitioning it to a sustainable system.

Session Organizer:

Erika Vanessa Wagner-Medina, AGROSAVIA, Colombia

Chair:

OSCAR A. FORERO, AGROSAVIA

Discussant:

Xavier Fargetton, Agrosavia

177. Methods and Materiality: Postphenomenological Studies

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

The postphenomenological perspective has been a presence in at 4S for years, and has featured multiple panels for more than a decade. This school of thought multiply overlaps with central STS theories, and perhaps most of all on the topic of the materiality of science and technology. In this panel we look to the future of postphenomenological research and explore and reconsider methodological issues. These include investigations into connections that can be made with both classical phenomenological insights, but also feminist new materialism and art theory. Don Ihde, the founder of postphenomenological analysis, begins this session with reflections on postphenomenology's STS-style case study methodology, and the patterns across scientific practice he has been able to articulate, especially regarding laboratory instrumental practices, here explored in terms of conventional and nano-scale microscopy. Galit Wellner follows with a paper on the under-examined connections waiting to be made between postphenomenological research and art theory and practice, with implications for our understandings of technological mediation and intentionality. Robert Scharff considers the technoscientific world that is presented to us through our various engagements with technology—from scientific instrumentation, to surgical expertise, to microtargeted disinformation campaigns—and he examines the resulting technoscientific standpoint and its implications for political resistance. And Róisín Lally explores the connections to be made between postphenomenological research and the feminist new materialist work of Karen Barad, and investigates the possible new ways that our future may be imagined.

Participants:

Postphenomenology and Art *Galit Wellner*, Tel Aviv University

Many postphenomenologists refer to works of arts in their writings, thereby following the phenomenologist tradition of Heidegger, Merleau-Ponty and others. A first look might give the impression that the works of arts are brought as mere examples of complex principles. A deeper examination reveals how art plays a major role in postphenomenology. In this paper, I map the various references to art in the context of philosophy of technology. First is the positioning of art as a better explanation of the postphenomenological relations. This is how Stan Kranc (2017) explains background relations with Roadsworth's Footprint (2003). The Footprint functions as a crosswalk in the shape of a giant footprint and can be best depicted from above. Second, art serves as a technology-intensive field, similarly to the scientific one. Don Ihde's analyses of prehistoric cave drawings (2017) and the implementation of the camera obscura by Renaissance artists (2012) exemplify this type of references. There is no art without technology, just as there is no science without technology. Third, art as a flexible way of thinking absorbs the newest technological ideas thereby creating what Ihde terms "pluriculture" (1990). Fourth, in some cases art functions as a harbinger for technology, as in the case of the impressionists who painted shadows in blue and green instead of grey, thereby preceding the digital representation in pixels of various colors (Ihde 1990, 47-8). Likewise, Peter-Paul Verbeek (2008) refers to new technologies of artistic photography to demonstrate the emergence of new technological intentionalities.

Our "World": A Matter for Post-Husserlian Reflection *Robert C. Scharff*, University of New Hampshire

Changes in our technologies obviously alter how we "see" our world, and with these changes come reconceptualizations of what we think "world" means. Postphenomenologists have been especially good at showing that this process is not just a matter of

better data leading to better theories about "the" world; nor is it even exclusively a technologized "knowledge" process. It is certainly true that Aristotle's cosmos, Newton's Nature, and today's Universe enframe our surroundings in ways so different that one is hard-pressed to find even family resemblances. But it is not just these world-concepts that are different. In each case, humans had to differently understand themselves as being-in and knowing about precisely such a world. How we understand our surroundings and how we understand ourselves vary together. So technoscientific change affects not just our conception of the world but also of the lives that can possibly be lived in it. Husserl thought of himself as being on the side of the angels for embracing the implicit "norms" of this world. So do many post-Husserlians. But what stops this embrace from also being scientifically elitist? And ontologically reductive? And politically undesirable? Who benefits and who loses when physical/chemical and biological/sociological truth overrule the "common understanding" of deficient knowers? Certainly, it often should. But does the global sense of "world" and "people" that derives from Husserl's Enlightenment imagery deserve the cultural hegemony it widely enjoys? Finally, from what philosophical standpoint are these questions best asked and answered?

A Matter for Postphenomenology: Spacetime matters and Feminism *Róisín Lally*, Gonzaga University

This paper is about the ontogenesis of being that entangles ideas in materiality. Because atoms make up the smallest particles of material reality, it is also a story about space and time. Physicist and philosopher Karen Barad calls this triplet "spacetime matters" or "time-being." Exploring the significance of our time, she develops her theory of diffraction, which exposes generational histories that exist retroactively. By tracing entanglements of violent histories of colonialism (with its practice of erasure and avoidance), she develops an ethics of a "justice-to-come" as an integral part of an embodied practice for re-membering, which is not about going back to what was but, rather, about the material reconfiguring of being-time in ways that produce new possible histories by which things might find ways to endure. This is not the progressive linear logic of capitalism, but a logic of dynamism that requires us to think imaginatively about the past as part of our future history, which we find in the works of postphenomenology and feminism.

Session Organizer:

Robert Rosenberger, Georgia Institute of Technology

178. Practices and Methods of Repair and Maintenance of Cultural Media - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

In recent years STS scholars have turned toward maintenance and repair as vital but overlooked responsibilities necessitated by our increasingly interconnected world. By foregrounding the banal – even boring – work of maintenance and repair, historians, theorists ethnographers, and others have exposed the constant effort that goes into preserving the functionality of everything from the vast sociotechnical assemblages of interstate highways to small, localized issues of personal comfort and bodily politics raised by air conditioning. Yet STS scholars have not yet made serious engagements with the maintenance and repair of cultural media, whose symbolic dimensions are typically left to media studies scholars. While interdisciplinary border crossings between STS and Media have increased, the wholesale digitization of media technologies demands that STS scholars contend with when, how, where, and why cultural media like paintings, radio, film and TV, games, and social media are repaired and maintained. This panel seeks to promote good relations between these two fields, bringing together questions of visibility and invisibility, labor, and innovation central to STS inquiries into repair and maintenance practices with questions of power and communication central to Media Studies. Themes to be explored in this panel might include but are not limited to: 1. Preservation and conservation of media artifacts 2. Sociotechnical repair

and maintenance in archival collections 3. Digitization and the maintenance of media access 4. Fan and user resistance and repair practices 5. Software maintenance and algorithmic repair 6. Repairing trust and truth in social media 7. Maintenance, repair, and normalization

Participants:

Repairing Media Technologies: Toward a Hybrid Methodology

Logan Brown, Indiana University; Marina Fontolan; Alexander John Daniel Mirowski, Indiana University

There has been a turn in STS research in recent years away from stories about innovation and progress and toward the mundane and invisible labor of maintenance and repair. This turn has yielded excellent research on the sociotechnical politics of maintenance, repair, and breakdown in software maintenance, public transportation, infrastructure development, and many other technologies. Yet STS has faltered in its approach to the maintenance and repair of media objects, whose symbolic dimension sits uneasily with STS methodologies. We argue that it is imperative that STS scholars interrogate how and why the maintenance and repair of a diesel engine is and is not equivalent to that of a Space Invaders arcade cabinet. This presentation offers the first steps toward a hybrid methodology for the study of the maintenance and repair of media by combining STS's empirical rigor and focus on the co-construction of the social and the technical with Media Studies' criticality and focus on the symbolic. Drawing examples from game studies, media studies, and software history we demonstrate that repair and maintenance of media objects always incorporates a necessarily normative symbolic dimension which differs from the ostensibly functional dimension of most other technologies. As the wholesale digitization of media raises questions of both centralization and decentralization, server maintenance and fan edits, it behooves us as STS scholars to augment the explanatory power we bring to bear in examining the maintenance and repair of an equally important category of technologies: those of human creativity and expression.

Data Practices And Sociotechnical Judgments Of Web Archives

Infrastructures Emily Maemura, University of Toronto

Web archives collections capture online cultural heritage and are increasingly of interest for historical scholarship, media studies, as well as a range of researchers and the general public. Many libraries are now using crawling software to collect websites and pages which act as important sociotechnical infrastructures for selecting, curating, and storing archived web data. Additionally, researchers using these collections face challenges in curating, selecting and analyzing large-scale datasets, as well as navigating legal limitations and varying access policies. Using the lens of infrastructure ethnography, this paper explores the data practices used in web archives collections and emerging humanities research infrastructures at two sites in Denmark and Canada. This work therefore extends 'laboratory studies' approaches to examine libraries, archives and cultural heritage collections as sites of knowledge production. The analysis of these cases highlights how digital curation is always inherently categorical work, requiring interpretation and negotiation of the categories inherent in digital materials, computational systems, and organizational policies. The study reveals how data practices are impacted by the materiality and scale of datasets, the affordances of computational systems and algorithmic logics used to delegate decisions, and the expertise of individual curators in enacting sociotechnical judgments upon data. Findings additionally locate where data categories are incompatible when translated between systems, how the reliance on standards renders aspects curation illegible, and where decisions are made both with and outside of algorithmic systems. As a contribution to critical data studies, new approaches applying archival theory principles are explored to describe sociotechnical contexts of data.

Saving Evil Sites: Preserving Digital Artifacts on Reddit Deleted for Community Violations *Matthew Robert*

Stapleton, University of Central Florida

The deletion of Internet communities on Reddit is often done for the protection of both the company as well as the userbase. Major subreddits such as r/The_Donald have been deleted for political extremism, while others like r/punchablefaces have been banned for hate speech and violence. The records of these subreddits still exist because of the efforts by external groups such as r/undelete and the WayBackMachine, which provide scholars with valuable resources in order to continue the study of these Internet communities. I believe that the tools themselves warrant discussion, particularly with regards to what companies like Reddit can do in order to preserve digital artifacts better. In order to properly analyze these resources, the selection of different deleted communities will be compared to the Internet traffic and usage of WayBackMachine and the subscriber and submission counts of r/undelete. Additionally, the spread of these displaced communities will also be traced, particularly in the case of r/The_Donald on the external website TheDonald.win, in order to better understand the mindset of such users towards their original platforms. I believe that deleting subreddits without proper digital archival techniques can impact how communities disperse afterwards, and that digital media companies such as Reddit need to properly enable the preservation of such data for future use and research.

'A Lot Of You Wanted Me To Talk About This': Moderating Relatability And Aesthetic Entrepreneurship In The Instagram #fitfam. *Louise M Ryan, University of Limerick*

This research provides significant insights into broad social science inquiry relating to the role of platforms in the establishment of new cultural authorities. I examine the relationship between influencers and the Instagram platform. Adopting a critical feminist lens this research makes visible the technological processes that are deemed by users 'unexplainable'. Revealing a value system that reinforces structural inequalities and fortifies exclusionary cultural trends while enabling the performance of entrepreneurial femininity. The walkthrough method provided data and visible features for analysis that are embedded in the Instagram platform bringing an 'ethnographic sensibility' to non-visible systems (Marcus 1999 p. 383). This study included analysis of screen recordings that captured installation, activation and usage of the app. Videos followed the user-end process of profile registration, set-up, and everyday use. This identified the 'field' of study and how the app's creators "expect users to receive and integrate it" in their everyday use (Light, Burgess, & Duguay, 2016). Close technical analysis of the Instagram platform alongside interviews with influencers and users identifies three themes specific to influencers and their efforts to build and retain a following. Here, the labour and self-regulation required contradicts the messages influencers share with their followers. Revealing an inequitable system embedded in the influencer industry, enacted, and reproduced through influencers' presentation strategies. The relationship cultivated between influencers and platforms is reflective of structural inequalities within a neoliberal attention economy upholding imbalances of power. Simultaneously, platform users increasingly demand more transparency concerning algorithms and data privacy within the social media industry.

Session Organizer:

Alexander John Daniel Mirowski, Indiana University

Chair:

Logan Brown, Indiana University

179. Artificial Intelligence in global perspective: inequalities, changing relations, governance - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

This panel aims to generate comparative insights into the ways in which AI technologies are debated, developed, applied and governed around the

world. Developments in AI, machine learning, and big data are transforming societies, the relationships of humans to each other, and interactions with the environment. Simultaneously, the deployment of AI, AI-based robots and smart information systems takes place in a context of global inequalities and competition, as well as well differences in cultural values, political systems and scientific capacities. In this panel we welcome contributions that explore aspects of the following questions: (i) What role do global inequalities and differences play in terms of how AI systems are developed, used and discussed in different global contexts? (ii) Which region-specific and shared global challenges emerge with regard to the governance of AI, AI-based robots and smart information systems? (iii) What are the effects of AI technologies on issues related to equality, diversity, justice and inclusion/exclusion around the world? (iv) What are the implications of the global adoption and use of AI systems for STS, and the ways in which relations between humans, data, intelligent machines and the (social and natural) environment are conceptualised and governed? The panel invites conceptual, theoretical and empirical contributions from across the world, with a particular interest in perspectives from Africa, Asia, the Middle East, Central and South America as well Oceania. Contributions that explore transnational developments or the effects of the international transfer of AI technologies from Europe and Northern America are also welcome.

Participants:

Algorithmic Technologies With Chinese Characteristics *Adrian Wong, UIUC*

Working within the culturally and technologically articulated spaces of algorithmic models, think tanks shape national and transnational policy design by producing and disseminating situationally inflected discourses. As brokers of scientific and political knowledge, these organizations interpret and frame software-hardware development in order to model the various uses and impacts of algorithms, artificial intelligence and smart infrastructure technology world-wide. The constant struggle for policy to keep up with technological development reveals critical questions for research on think tank discourse and communication strategies. What data, as evidence, do think tanks index as a foundation to build their own prediction models on the ways in which artificial intelligence will “disrupt” the global order? What are the primary “nodal discourses” around which policy papers, speeches, presentations and reports are clustering? Do globally networked think tanks create communication fault lines, which fracture the discursive ecology either according to geo-political divisions, “discursive coalitions,” or cultural stratifications, and if so, how do these fault lines structure the discursive terrain of think tank communication practice? This article applies critical discourse analysis and digital ethnographic methods to interpret how think tanks produce evidence on the future imaginaries of technology, index data, enregister globally scaled social positionalities and entextualize a global order through documents and multi-modal communicative forms on- and off-line. It takes the discourses of China- and Asian-based think tanks working on the Digital Silk Road as a point of departure. Such communication foreshadows geo-political shifts and narrates causal relationships produced around a culturally inflected vision of AI.

Technological Pilot Meets Development Project in Tanzanian Rice Fields - A Process of Translation *Astrid Matejcek*

Against the backdrop of food security, allegedly untapped agricultural potential and pursuing a Green Revolution for Africa, international NGOs remain important intermediaries for the transfer of agricultural science and technologies. Realizing the limited transferability of Western technologies to the Global South, they shift to “trial and error” approaches to generate adapted innovations. In this context the pilot project of the Spatio-Temporal Agribusiness Support System (STASS) conducted in a trial community in Southern Tanzania serves in this presentation to critically reflect on the adoption of AI systems in rural Africa. Taking up Tilley’s idea of ‘Africa as a Living Laboratory’, I will show how the project attempts to

“develop” both the community and the technology itself. Based on long-term ethnographic research concerning the application of the digital drone and satellite-based information technology, I examine the logics and (unintended) effects of translating a technological pilot into a development project. Focusing on changing actor constellations, knowledge productions and everyday practices in relation to the AI system reveals the inequalities embedded in mobile connectivity, information-based autonomous decision-making, and technology-led local problem-solving. Through such pilot projects AI systems are being adapted to expand their markets and algorithms to environments in the Global South, however, the ethnographic insights also point to how the rather neglected farmers still take advantage of the live laboratory by appropriating provided information as they see fit. This contribution highlights how experimenting for technological innovations and development reinforces inequalities, and yet AI systems do not necessarily act in an exclusive manner.

Session Organizer:

Achim Rosemann, De Montfort University, UK

Chair:

Lizette Huezio-Ponce, Tecnológico de Monterrey

180. Rethinking Expertise: A New Look at Digitization and Decentralization I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Participants:

Data Divergence And Data Ideology From Fukushima To The Pandemic in Japan *Ina Kim, University of California - Irvine*

This ethnographic research examines data divergence and data ideology constructed in particular contexts of the Fukushima disaster and the COVID-19 pandemic in Japan. Since the Fukushima nuclear disaster, more than 50 citizen radiation detection laboratories have been established to produce, analyze, modify, and circulate their own radiation data due to data distrust in the Japanese government. While the citizen scientists are still engaged in the radiation detection data activism, the COVID-19 pandemic demands another, but consistent kind of data divergence. The Japanese government has been criticized for controlling the numbers of domestic positive cases in hopes of hosting the Olympics and upholding their international image. In response to this criticism, citizen scientists started collecting data on cases of “refused testing” or “testing unavailable.” Some of the citizen data platforms originally producing radiation data now also provide or analyze COVID-19 data. This study sheds light on how the continuation of distinctive disaster data practices build citizen data communities, reinforce anti-neoliberal data ideology, and gain scientific and political authorities in knowledge production. These data practices fill the gaps between official data and the knowledge that citizens need and ultimately help relieve uncertainty and anxiety of citizens in the aftermath of disasters. Participant-observation, interviews, archival research, and online discourse analysis have been conducted to explore the data practices of citizen scientists in Japan. This paper contributes to uncovering how data practices of different, but connected, disaster communities are shaped, shared, and contested in the era of uncertainty.

From Epistemic Collaboration to Epistemic Domination: The Flint Water Crisis, Citizen Scientism, and the Myth of the “Tribal” Public *Yanna Lambrinidou, Virginia Tech; Ben Pauli, Kettering University*

This paper examines the expansion of Citizen Science from a practice that is science-centered, in enlisting non-experts to collect data that advance scientific research, to a practice that is also society-centered, in fostering scientist-community collaborations to generate knowledge that advances the public good. Focusing on the period when this expansion was first

articulated and celebrated, the paper examines Citizen Science's imaginary of its 'entrance' into society and its effort to forge a "new relationship between scientists and the public." It pays particular attention to the selection at the time of a specific citizen science project — underway in Flint, Michigan — as Citizen Science's "gold standard" of democratic, trust-filled, and societally impactful scientist-community collaborations and as the embodiment of Citizen Science's society-centered promise. Four years later, however, evidence shows that the Flint project quickly devolved from epistemic collaboration to epistemic domination, whereby community voices were discounted, unless they echoed the voices of the scientists, and community attempts to reassert epistemic independence were ridiculed and punished. The paper posits that in its very launch of a transformative relationship with society, Citizen Science turned itself into a vehicle for scientific knowledge-making that reified the existing social order, wherein power, authority, purity, and truth reside with scientists and are threatened by non-deferential publics. It also highlights a fundamental risk in Citizen Science's new 'society-centered' frontier: the bolstering of Citizen Science and its practitioners at the expense of transdisciplinary research that can better position communities to address the complex socio-technical problems affecting their lives.

The Role of Citizens in a Pandemic: Expertise and Credibility Contests in the News Media *Sonja Erikainen, University of Edinburgh; Ellen Stewart*

During the early months of the COVID-19 pandemic, citizens quickly began to take collective action to mitigate the disruptive impact of the pandemic on healthcare systems and citizens' lives. This included citizen-led en masse production of face masks and hand sanitisers, which was partially motivated by perceived inadequacies in governments' pandemic mitigation efforts, including personal protective equipment shortages. Much citizen mobilisation was facilitated by digital era developments that provide citizens with unprecedented access and ability to harness scientific knowledge and to rapidly mobilise large collectives online. Citizen-led pandemic mitigation efforts exemplify wider shifts in the articulations of the roles of citizens in science, including public health science, where citizens are increasingly taking active roles including via citizen- and DIY science activities. Concurrently, the epistemic authority of professional scientific and health 'experts' has been increasingly contested in public discourses and popular media, including via credibility contests over the contributions that citizens can or should make to health-related innovation. This paper focuses on media debates around citizen-led pandemic mitigation in Europe and North America, taking discourse analysis of newspaper representations around citizens making DIY face masks and hand sanitisers as a lens to explore wider questions around the changing ways in which the roles of citizens in public health are delineated and represented under conditions of significant scientific uncertainty. This will illuminate wider shifts in the roles of citizens in public health science in the digital era, where the epistemic authority of professional 'experts,' including public health authorities, is also unstable.

Session Organizer:

Emine Onculer Yayalar, Bilkent University

Chair:

Melike Sahinol, Orient-Institut Istanbul

Discussant:

Erkan Saka, İstanbul Bilgi University

181. Teaching Science and Engineering for Social Justice – II

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Science and engineering education bear significant responsibility in fostering democratic and just technoscientific practice, especially given the complicity of technoscience in several social injustices. For example, AI-

based surveillance has reinforced the marginalization of minorities, while the use of toxic chemicals in the electronics industry has caused several worker miscarriages. However, pressured by a market-driven system that prioritizes technical skills, this responsibility is often relegated to ethics or STS courses that are separated from the core science/engineering curriculum. Further, as Dr. Timnit Gebru's recent exit from Google illustrates, the environments of professional technoscience are often themselves averse to critically analyzing issues of social justice and ethics in their practice. Consequently, science and engineering students seldom learn how to engage with social justice as it relates to the subject-matter and methods of technoscience. This is problematic as it can promote agnosticism or even antagonism towards considering the role of technoscience in perpetuating social injustices and inequity. How can we teach science/engineering for social justice in a system that often devalues social justice? In this panel, we invite submissions that critically engage with this question through theoretical and/or practical work. Examples include but are not limited to (re)designing and discussing: • Classroom strategies, courses, or curricula • Digital educational media such as games, simulations, and information visualizations • Policies and power dynamics of the educational system • Personal narratives as educators, administrators, or students as they relate to the challenges of teaching science/engineering for social justice.

Participants:

Power in the Interface: teaching critical software interface design *Levin Kim, The Information School, University of Washington; Alannah Oleson, The Information School, University of Washington*

Students in many existing CS programs are underexposed to educational materials that challenge them to think critically about the technological artifacts they create. In particular, with interface design, there is a gap when it comes to resources that give students concrete strategies for understanding and designing for users with diverse abilities, perspectives, needs, and contexts (Oleson et al. 2020). This can lead to interfaces that only work well for a subset of the population, causing frustration at best and perpetuating harm at worst (c.f. Wittkower 2016, Costanza-Chock 2020). We present an educational technique that centers on the politics of the interface to give CS students concrete ways of thinking about how power gets translated into explicit and implicit design biases. It guides students to identify design biases in existing technological artifacts, consider scenarios of exclusion, and scaffolds generation of more inclusive redesign ideas while engaging with theoretical perspectives around social justice. This technique is grounded in prior work in HCI education, inclusive design, and feminist theory and pedagogy, and is intended for use in higher education human-computer interaction (HCI) design classes. Through a case study in a classroom setting, we demonstrate that this technique enables CS students to concretely grapple with abstract notions such as inclusion and social justice within their own work. By focusing on the interface as the site where power imbalances manifest as exclusionary designs, students are empowered to situate themselves within deeper conversations around technology and power that they carry long past the classroom itself. References: Alannah Oleson, Meron Solomon, and Amy J. Ko. 2020. Computing Students' Learning Difficulties in HCI Education. In Proceedings of the 2020 CHI Conference on Human Factors in Computing Systems (CHI '20). Association for Computing Machinery, New York, NY, USA, 1–14. DOI:https://doi.org/10.1145/3313831.3376149 D.E. Wittkower. 2016. Principles of Anti-Discriminatory Design. In 2016 IEEE International Symposium on Ethics in Engineering, Science and Technology (ETHICS), 1–7. DOI:https://doi.org/10.1109/ETHICS.2016.7560055 Sasha Costanza-Chock. 2020. Design Justice: Community-led practices to build the worlds we need. MIT Press.

Historicizing educational robot pedagogies as work towards justice in STEM education *Colin Hennessy Elliott; Deborah*

Silvis, Utah State University

Robots are becoming powerful tools in K-12 and informal learning settings. They are manifestations of particular theories of learning, which in turn construct particular kinds of learners. In this paper, we argue for historicizing educational robots by excavating the stories of their development and the futures they help imagine, a proleptic shift that brings past models of human cognition into the present in ways that are consequential for learning. We build with Philip and Sengupta's (2020) argument that "theories of learning are theories of society" together with Benjamin's call to make "techno scientific accounts of the world accountable... rather than allowing th[e] social infrastructure to remain invisible" (2017, p. 14). We examine two prominent forms of educational robots from our own research in STEM education: a coding robot toy for young children and a high school team's competition robot. Exploring these robot's histories-in-the-present, we ask what theories of learning they encode in their design and use and therefore what visions of society they make possible for learners who interact with them. While very different in their application, both robots' design narratives are deeply entangled with constructionism (Paper, 1980), which envisions a certain rugged individualism and focus on the technical (Ames, 2018). Further they align with militarized vision of an automated future workforce (Suchman, 2015; Vossoughi & Vakil, 2018). In order to make STEM education more equitable, we call for historicizing and remaking educational robots in the image of more just futures with the communities that use them.

Critical Pedagogy Meets Computer Science: Tensions Faced by Educators *Eric Mayhew; Elizabeth Patitsas, McGill University*

There is a clear need to improve computer science education to instill values of social justice, caring, environmentalism, sustainability, and good relations. New and radical pedagogues have been proposed for teaching computer science from a critical standpoint, reflecting influences from critical pedagogy (Freire, hooks, etc) and culturally responsive education. However, in our interviews with critical pedagogues we have found a theme of insufficient support and push back for using overtly political approaches to computing education. In this talk we report on interviews with 13 computing educators who self-described as being influenced by critical pedagogy. Common barriers reported by participants included: student push back, push back from administration, internal tension in our participants about what critical pedagogy is in a computing context, how to reconcile critical pedagogy with working within educational systems, and reconciling student-centered teaching when students' goals are to participate in the capitalist economy. Our talk will follow narratives of particular participants in order to illustrate the their struggles, tensions, and resolutions to some of the aforementioned issues. This will inform how critical pedagogy can be implemented in computing, and further professional development for computing educators who wish to tackle injustice in their teaching.

Towards Justice-Centered Critical Participation for Undergraduate Computer Scientists *Gabriel Medina-Kim, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute*

Given assimilationist criticism of national initiatives to expand computer science education, recent computing education research has called for its researchers and educators to reconsider their engagements with equity in computing through justice-centered approaches. This requires expanding conventional notions of equity so that interventions in equity do not end with broadening participation. Recognizing critical scholarship that calls for computer science and its educators to internalize how computing shapes and is shaped by society, critically engaging the racial and sociopolitical contexts of computing is a necessity for computing education. This paper

responds to such calls for action by demonstrating how computing educators can commit to justice-centered approaches to equity by using the author's development of an undergraduate computer science elective course as an example. The course plan is discussed through three facets: the course's purpose, its content, and its (intended) learning environment. Titled "Power, Equity, and Praxis in Computing," the purpose of the course is to make space for undergraduate computing students to explore how systems of power shape fields of computing so that students can practice making social justice-centered transformations as critical participants of their field. The content of the course plan is organized through modules that overview sites and considerations for intervention within computing. Through teacher-student partnerships that emboldens students to read and write (both code and written word) with computer science, science and technology studies, and anti-racist feminist studies, the author suggests that computing education draws on its interdisciplinarity to center justice within our research for equity.

Session Organizer:

Aditya Anupam, Georgia Institute Of Technology

182. The Prediction Factor: Medical Decision in the Age of Big Data - I: Big Data, prediction and health care: spreading or resistance ?

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

The literature often presents the use of Big Data in the health care setting as ineluctable but limits its focus on clinical care and at best include Internet of things devices. This last session will introduce other dimensions: the spreading and mapping of the technology outside was is traditionally anticipated (smart cities), but also counter examples under the "resistance" flag in practices.

Participants:

How is AI being used in Guangzhou to improve the healthcare sector *Zongtian Guo*

Cities around the world are piloting combinations of AI to develop cities. To date, many cities have created and implemented policies and programmes intended to transform them into smart city. The fundamental purpose of technologies is not only to make the city better but also to meet citizens' needs. More importantly, artificial intelligence technology can also improve healthcare effectiveness and lower healthcare cost for citizens. However, to date, there is a need to fill a gap in research on how to apply technologies to meet citizens' health needs. Using Guangzhou, the largest city in the south of China, as a case study, the research will examine how artificial intelligence technologies is applied in Guangzhou's smart city initiatives to meet the health needs of citizens. Research participants will include citizens in the Guangzhou metropolitan area (i.e., Guangzhou city; Foshan; Zhaoqing; Qingyuan; Yunfu; Shaoguan). The research will investigate how AI is transforming Guangdong's healthcare sector and the implementation of Guangzhou's AI healthcare sector. The study will also focus on how AI is being used by the local government to improve the healthcare level in Guangzhou. Overall, the findings of the research will contribute theoretically and empirically to the "AI in the healthcare sector" academic debate by providing a fuller and more critical understanding of the relationship between digital technologies and healthcare.

Resisting Big Data in Medical Decision-Making: The Case of Epilepsy *Megh Marathe, University of Michigan, Ann Arbor; Kentaro Toyama, University of Michigan*

Through the case of epilepsy, this paper examines seizure diagnosis as a situated, relational, and evolving processual instantiation of medical decision-making in the age of big data. The electroencephalogram (EEG) is widely considered to be a definitive yes-or-no test for seizures. State-of-the-art seizure detection systems, for example, apply machine learning

techniques to EEG data sets in order to differentiate seizure from non-seizure events. This paper examines how specialists negotiate such data-driven systems in practice, drawing upon fifteen months of ethnographic observation and interviews with epileptologists (neurologists who specialize in epilepsy). The paper shows that a lot of medical decision-making is based on contextual data that is not easily digitized. Further, the paper shows that doctors use behind-the-scenes workarounds to bend diagnostic categories, thereby producing numbers that help achieve prescriptive ends (e.g., customizing standardized treatment protocols to specific patients), while conforming to external pressures for data-driven decision-making. This demonstrates a particular kind of resistance to big data in routine medical practice.

The Medical Record: Digitisation and Oracular Power in Medical Practice *Max Edward Perry, University of Bistol*

As Medicine professionalised and specialised in the 19th and 20th century, a the Medical Record became a vital technology, that focused medical care around patients (as opposed to doctors). The Medical Record became a legal object organised around the ‘unit’ of the patient, then in the 1960s American physician Lawrence Weed argued successfully for the development of a ‘Problem Orientated Medical Record’ that focused care not on patients but on the empirical matter of patient problems. Weed described the Medical Record as ‘the scientist’s notebook’, it was a technology that ordered the empirical data accumulated during care to provide clarity of thought for the doctor, as well as clarity of audit for the profession. In the 21st century Digital Health initiatives promise transformation of this Medical Record, not just via digital datafication of a traditionally analogue object, but through the placing of patients into larger networks (of populations), to create new ways of knowing. From the scientist’s notebook to the scientists’ database. In this paper I will show how Digital Health initiatives fit into a history of professionalisation of medicine that looks to impose regularity on medical practice, and that a will-to-regulation has privileged a particular epistemic approach to medicine that is in conflict with contemporary medical practice. Focusing on a historical study of the NHS, and Secondary Care, I will show how the Medical Record has resisted transformation agendas, and how in this resistance we can see a struggle over ‘Oracular power’ in the practice of medicine.

The Data-Empowered Individual: Mythmaking For A Datafied Society *Santeri Räisänen, University of Helsinki, Center for Consumer Society Research*

The National Artificial Intelligence Programme AuroraAI is a visionary programme of social transformation, a techno-solutionistic fantasy, and a plastic context for constructing visions of welfare. The project aims to move Finland towards a “human-centric and predictive society” through a combination of technological interventions paired with a model of well-being centred around empowerment through data. While the project is centrally concerned with developing infrastructure for data collection, analysis and use, a puzzle among the actors in the project remains: what does “human-centered and predictive society” in fact mean, and how does AI figure into it? Based on my field research on the project, consisting of interviews, official documentation and internal presentations, I’ve traced the bricolage by which the narrative of AI and welfare has been constructed, and how the ambiguous and elastic justifications for the project are interpreted by the diverse actors involved. I focus on the stories, akin to a Barthesian mythology, in the making of this project of datafication. These are stories that situate the public sector in contrast to institutions of contemporary data capitalism, while at the same time enacting the same logics. Furthermore, these are stories which construct an ideal of the data-empowered individual, making the problem of welfare algorithmically solvable. Drawing on theory from STS, cultural studies and media studies, I aim to contribute to the discourse on

the co-production of technology and society, namely, in asking how myth takes part in the legitimation of a datafied society.

Session Organizer:

Marie Le Clainche Piel, CNRS - Centre d'Etude des Mouvements Sociaux

183. Unpacking The “Datafied” Society: Shifting Politics of Seeing and Knowing - II

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Participants:

A human-driven approach to “datafied” society *Ana Carolina Nunes, Oregon State University; Shaozeng Zhang, Oregon State University*

This paper is an initial report of our fair AI design project using big datasets by a small research team made up of anthropologists and computer scientists. Our collaborative project was developed in response to the recent debates on ethical and social issues of big data and AI (Elish and boyd 2018). We share this understanding that “numbers don't speak for themselves,” but data enter into research projects already “fully cooked” (D'Ignazio and Klein 2020). Therefore, we take an anthropological approach to observing, recording, understanding, and reflecting upon the process of machine learning algorithm design since the first steps of choosing and coding datasets for training and building algorithms. We tease apart the encoding of social-cultural paradigms in the generation and use of datasets in algorithm design and testing. By doing so, we rediscover the human in data to challenge the methodological and social assumptions in data use and adjust the model and parameters of our algorithms. This paper centers on tracing the Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions' social trajectory, knows as the COMPAS dataset. This dataset contains data of over 10,000 criminal defendants in Broward County in Florida, the U.S. Since its publication, it has become a landmark dataset in the study of algorithmic fairness and was also used to design and train our algorithm for recidivism prediction. This paper presents our observation that data results from a complex set of social, political, and historical assumptions and circumstances and demonstrates a human-driven approach to data use and an increasingly “datafied” society.

Conformity and Obfuscation: Infrapolitics of Impression Management under Data-driven State Surveillance *Alex Jiahong Lu, University of Michigan; Yuchen Chen*

In China, the growth and expansion of data-driven surveillance infrastructure make the data collection and processing on citizen’s financial and non-financial activities (social credit system), health status (Covid-19 health code system), and more. The recent implementation of the state-owned platform XueXi QiangGuo (hereinafter, XueXi) has expanded the China’s surveillance capabilities to the domain of political communication and engagement. In particular, individuals who work in the public sector and members of the Chinese Communist Party network have been mandated to actively engage in XueXi. Individuals’ use of the system is quantified, tracked, and thereby evaluated by the state. Through the observation and interviews with 28 active XueXi users, we seek to investigate citizens’ everyday interactions with the platform and how individuals perform impression management online under state surveillance for political communication. Through Erving Goffman's dramaturgical lens, we uncover individuals' everyday socio-technical practices of conforming to and obfuscating surveillance as ways of impression management to the state. Our work unpacks how these practices help us rethink both individuals' relations to data-driven surveillance practices and state surveillance in China. We contribute to STS scholarship in three ways: 1) foregrounding users' calculation, complicity, and agency and challenge dominant thinking of China's state

surveillance being oppressive and top-down and the ever-shifting infrapolitics of individuals under surveillance as termed by James Scott, 2) presenting a different understanding of impression management with the context of increasing datafication in surveillance practices, and 3) providing an alternative narrative to understand the state-citizen relationship in the context of state surveillance.

Sampling and sense making: data journeys in the clinic *Usha Raman, University of Hyderabad*

Scholars have sought to understand the processes of turning the body into data, which have bearing on how quantifiable information is generated, the logics by which it is analyzed, integrated, and read, ultimately constituting the implicit framework within which medical meaning emerges. The practices of numbering which are based on different assumptions, the manner in which numbers are bundled together and then acted upon algorithmically is an important concern in health data, particularly in relation to understanding what we may call “data journeys” (Bates, Liu and Goodale, 2016). This approach, deriving from an STS perspective and drawing on Actor-Network Theory, calls for us to locate critical data studies in health and other fields within contexts of data production, transmission, agglomeration and analysis, if we are to understand how it constructs and informs the “data gaze” (Beer, D, 2018), and how meaning shifts as the data move from interpretive field to another. This paper explores these data journeys from the point of extraction/abstraction from the embodied individual through the laboratory or diagnostic service to the clinician, to understand the ways in which meaning is produced, reproduced, interpreted and finally applied back to the understanding and management of the body.

The Visible Body and the Invisible Organization: Data, Labor, and Authority in Elite Athletics *Daniel Greene, University of Maryland; Nathan Beard, University of Maryland*

Elite athletes are constantly tracked, measured, scored, and sorted in order to improve their performance. Datafication is pursued in the name of gaining a competitive edge. Privacy is sacrificed in the name of incremental improvement, but athletes frequently do not know why particular personal data are being monitored or what is done with them. In the largest US universities, athletics is also a big business. These universities justify the datafication of athletes' health and performance through their stewardship of student safety and security in the name of their educational futures, in loco parentis. Student-athletes are nominally there to learn, but there is more knowledge produced about their bodies than they are permitted to see. Our interview study of 50 Division 1 college athletes and athletics staff members reveals that their sportsplay is governed by an experience of information asymmetry, but that this asymmetry looks different for different sports with different levels of investment, different racial and gender makeups, and different performance metrics. Theories of privacy and scholarship on personal data generally focus their analysis on individual rights-bearing subjects (e.g., consumers, users, plaintiffs). But the most consequential data collected from us, with the greatest effect on our lives, is frequently a product of collective engagement with specific organizational contexts like workplaces and schools. As they negotiate these information asymmetries, our participants show that privacy must always be considered a collective endeavor and that research on the quantified self must address the quantified organization.

Postulated Consumers – Co-producing datafied knowledge about consumers in marketing *Roger von Laufenberg, Vienna Centre for Societal Security*

The proliferation of big data analytics (BDA) appears to have significant effects on many areas, radically changing the way knowledge is being co-produced and how that knowledge is being used. Here, I focus on the use of BDA in marketing, more specifically on how BDA is used to conceptualise consumers.

Relying on interviews with marketers and analysts, case studies, and participant observations at industry conferences, I show how marketers are not satisfied with approximate, imagined conceptualisations of consumers. Instead, they are looking for exact data doubles, something they hope to achieve through BDA. I explore the question of how and why marketers conceptualise consumers differently when using BDA compared with traditional consumer research methods, and how this shapes how marketers act on consumers. The data double consumer is considered ideal, believed to be made possible through BDA, expected to create an exact knowledge about consumers. However, in practice, BDA should be considered a sociotechnical assemblage, producing knowledge which contains inaccuracies, errors, and uncertainties. Knowledge is not just discovered but is the outcome of a co-production (Jasanoff 2006) that involves different individuals, teams, normativities, and technologies. Hence, knowledge is never an exact representation of reality, irrespective of its methods of production. Consequently, consumer conceptualisations expected to be exact data doubles cannot be attained. Instead, postulations are established that are believed to be accurate, without having actual proof. Yet, my findings show that knowledge resulting from BDA has more epistemic authority amongst the participants, explaining the persistence of the data double.

Session Organizer:

Srravya C, IIT Bangalore

184. Drone Studies Meetup

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Drones have become both important tools and objects of analysis across numerous sites and contexts of STS research. Whether used to monitor wildlife populations, undertake archaeological surveys or wage war, drones present unique challenges and opportunities for STS researchers. And while there are crucial differences across these many contexts, there are also valuable commonalities to explore. This virtual meetup aims to breakdown the silos of drone studies research in STS and establish good relations across the varied practices and methods through which drones enter the frame of research. It will be a chance to raise questions, share stories and learn from one another, with the aim of establishing stronger networks of STS researchers working to understand drone technologies in all their many forms and applications.

Session Organizer:

Michael Richardson, University of New South Wales

Chair:

Adam Fish, University of New South Wales

185. Equality By Design Vs Design For Appropriation In Digital Resource Sharing - II

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Several scholars in STS (in platform and infrastructure studies, Plantin et al. 2018; see also in Internet studies, Dulong de Rosnay and Musiani 2020) have pointed to architectural features of profit-driven global digital infrastructures, e.g., GAFAM, that lead to concentrations of power, discrimination and inequalities. Conversely, egalitarian applications such as on-line peer-to-peer production platforms tend to fail the test of scaling up small communities of participants to egalitarian dynamics in large groups, thus sometimes falling back into profit-driven, hierarchical, and discriminatory modes of operation (Tréguer et al. 2020). The panel proposes to consider the problem of (in-)equalities and discrimination in information- (and possibly other resource-) sharing systems not as a consequence of system structure nor platform usage; rather, we encourage taking the opposite perspective: can inequalities be avoided from the outset. How can discrimination be hindered by the design of adequate architecture mechanisms for equality? What is the role of STS scholars in engaging with the design phase of systems? The panel invites empirical contributions where equality is considered, negotiated, contested in a system's architecture as an initial design value. The user communities of these

systems need not to be large, nor their mode of function to be peer-to-peer. Contributions are invited to describe how the value of equality was designed in these projects and how it was to be integrated in, promoted by, or supported by the system's architecture.

Participants:

(Pre)judices of homoconnectivity in Ecuador by design on Grindr
Pedro Andrés Gutiérrez Guevara, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

This empirical investigation around virtual presence of gay and bisexual mens, trans and queer persons in Grindr evidence the increasing of homoconnectivity in Ecuador. The over time from the decriminalization of homosexuality in Ecuador in 1997 towards the use of interfaces and applications have modified the forms of languages, exclusions and relationships. Grindr as a platform is a programmable digital architecture designed to organize interactions between users not just end users but also corporate entities and public bodies. The actual design of the application is far from being neutral because this model the behaviour and "needs" for GBTQ users. The conceptual marc where this presentation take reflexion is prejudiced violence, tecnoliberalism and datafication which creates a process of mercantilization of GBTQ identity who at the same time makes possible exclusionary interaction. Through hate speech make loud the presence of misogyny, racism, xenophobia and serophobia anchored in binary narratives of active/passive, camp/manly, visible/invisible and health/unhealthy bodies. The technology of Grindr enables users to introduce: age, height, weight, ethnic origin, sexual rol (top, bottom or versatile), tribes, love situation, expectations, gender identity, HIV status and pin social media. This personal data is used during the interaction for digital violences and discriminations. This presentation use: interviews and reflections of gay and queer activists from Cuenca, Guayaquil and Quito and personals screenshots as a user from 2018-2020 to describe and think the political, economic, legal and technological changes of Grindr as an infrastructure who increase the possibilities of control.

Flipping the Script: Testing the Limits of Knowing Platforms
Ana Pop Stefanija, imec-SMIT, Vrije Universiteit Brussel; Jo Pierson, VUB

If our online and offline lives, interactions and opportunities have been increasingly guided by "all-knowing" platforms with their algorithmic and ADM systems, what happens when we flip the scripts? When the "gazed-upon" gaze back? More importantly, how can we, if at all, overturn the epistemic power imbalances and what happens next? Faced with the opacity of these systems, loss of knowledge and understanding how these platforms work and impact individuals' lives stripping them of agency, we conducted a participatory research in an attempt to "gaze back" and (methodologically) test ways of knowing platforms. Working around with the affordances of both the platforms and the regulatory tools in place, we conducted a research with 47 participants. Using the Right of Access granted under the Article 15 of the General Data Protection Regulation, as well as the transparency tools of the sampled platforms, the participants were able to inspect what platform know about them and how. They recorded their experience, interactions and reflections in a structured research diary, outlining additionally their requirements for trust and algorithmic agency. The insights collected help both us, as researchers, and the participants as users, to contemplate on the ways to know platforms and the scope and limits of the possible knowledge. Critically reflecting on the methodological opportunities, challenges and limitation of flipping the scripts, this paper aims to outline possible strategies for mitigating existing power asymmetries and propose specific infrastructural, design and policy recommendations for user agency and empowerment.

Institutional analysis of platforms and their sociotechnical characteristics
Javier de Rivera, Universidad de Vigo; Ángel

Gordo López, Universidad Complutense de Madrid

We understand digital platforms as institutions that socialize users through their socio-technical designs, conforming their subjectivity in accordance to certain norms, values and world views. This presentation will address several researches about how the design of software architectures affects social interactions. First, a netnographic study conducted on 55 platforms of the so called collaborative economy, establishing a typology of platforms based on the impact of their systems in social relations (de Rivera et al, 2016). The type of platforms such as Airbnb are designed to help users promote their social capital and profit from it, while others focus on plain efficiency, and a third type had an orientation towards community building. A few years later, we expanded this research taking in account the sustainability/business models of these platforms, finding out that profit driven platforms tend to stimulate a competitive social environment, usually through the emphasis on ratings and virtual reputation, a feature designed to reduce the management costs of the system. On the other hand, platforms orientated towards social values implemented features that produce more egalitarian relations as well as more inclusive environments (de Rivera, 2019). In addition, we applied a similar approach on social media platforms, considering how the structural interests of their admins/owners affect their design, and therefore their impact on how people interact (Gordo et. al. 2018). In the presentation we will summarize our findings and conclusions on how systems' design can promote more egalitarian and inclusive digital environments. de Rivera, J., Gordo, A., Cassidy, P. & Apesteuguía, A. (2017). A netnographic study of P2P collaborative consumption platforms' user interface and design. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 23, 11-27. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.eist.2016.09.003>

Mapping the Landscape of Sharing and Cooperativism for Design Research and Practice
Özge Subaşı, Koç University; Anton Fedosov, University of Zurich; Oliver Bates, Lancaster University

Emerging studies of local cooperatives, their sharing practices, and the use of platforms for cooperation call for specific designs and design guidelines to support the endurance and growth of the community-oriented collaborative economy. These efforts also indicate that design has the potential to shape cooperative engagements. However, to-date, only a few design resources are tailored for exploring and further developing design insights from empirical and conceptual research on sharing and cooperativism. To bridge this gap, we report on an international workshop that included a diverse group of scholars, designers, and activists. During the workshop, we aimed to unpack the role of design regarding sharing and cooperativism. Through the synthesis of workshop outcomes, we present new insights pointing towards the development an ecosystemic approach in design for cooperativism. We call on designers to (1) proactively adopt design goals that focus on ecosystemic design and tools; (2) be inclusive, equitable, and justice-oriented to ensure solidarity and collectivism; and (3) rethink terms such as, currency and data while designing for cooperativism in their projects. In this paper, we conceptualise and discuss the key ideas from the workshop highlighting potential implications for design research and practice.

Session Organizers:

*Léa Maria Stiefel, Unil
Alain Sandoz, IIUN*

Discussants:

*Léa Maria Stiefel, Unil
Alain Sandoz, IIUN*

186. Forensic Evidence And Expertise In Local, National And Global Contexts - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Forensic evidence is collected, analysed and rendered meaningful by different actors using various technologies and expertise. A powerful resource in the investigation of crime, STS scholars have paid substantial attention to the development, standardisation, enactment and use of specific forensic technologies (namely fingerprinting and forensic DNA profiling). These accounts demonstrate the complex expertise and labour involved in producing and using forensic evidence, and the many local and national contexts that impact on how the legitimacy and value of specific types of forensic evidence are negotiated over time. Beyond fingerprinting and DNA, there are many other types of forensic evidence. Some have long histories, like fibre analysis. Others, such as digital forensics, are newer and continually evolving, keeping pace and responding to the latest technological developments. In this panel, we invite papers that examine empirically the varied actors, labour and expertise involved in the production and use of other types of forensic evidence in the investigation and prosecution of crime. We are particularly interested in accounts that engage with how forensic evidence and expertise are negotiated in specific local, national and/or global law enforcement contexts and the related areas of overlap and convergence. This panel contributes to STS scholarship on the intersections between science, law and law enforcement, standardisation in scientific practice, and the negotiation of expertise across the different epistemic cultures of criminal justice systems.

Participants:

Race, pathology, and "habitual" crime in the primitive accumulation of forensic power *Fiona Greenland, University of Virginia; Madeleine Peterson, University of Virginia*
Fingerprinting was one of the earliest forms of forensic evidence in US law enforcement work. Prior STS scholarship has documented how, by the late 19th century, most fingerprint experts reluctantly accepted that fingerprint patterns were not classifiable by race. This paper builds on that scholarship to show how medicalization and privatization enabled fingerprint experts to racialize their work differently. Ingeniously, even as fingerprint advocates conceded that fingerprint patterns were not classifiable by race or ethnicity, they suggested that the best way to establish and control Black and brown people's supposed "inherent criminality" was by fingerprinting. We draw on extensive early 20th century materials from the Chicago Police Department, the United States Penitentiary at Leavenworth, Kansas, circuit and district court transcripts, period newspapers, and the Institute for Applied Science, a Chicago-based for-profit school that brought forensic training to the American public. We show that forensic expertise was deliberately broken up and distributed between public and private sectors. Independent "Fingerprint Men" straddled both domains, and served as zealous enforcers of (white majority) social norms even as they were legitimized to "translate" forensic evidence for multiple audiences. Public officials, including fingerprint experts based in police departments and prisons, used the Fingerprint Men's sensational "whodunits?" to develop classifications and vocabulary that claimed to link crime, fingerprints, and sickness. Local-level interactions were crucial to this work. The developments we document, from about 1905 to 1940, laid the groundwork for contemporary mass surveillance and the powerful role of private sector interests in developing surveillance capital.

Producing Robust Forensic Evidence In Routine Crime Scene Examination *David Wyatt, King's College London*

There are numerous actors involved in the police use of forensic science. While the Crime Scene Examiner (CSE) is visible in the public image of forensic science, STS scholarship has often ignored the complex work of the CSE in facilitating the meaningful use of forensic science and forensic evidence in police work. In this paper, I focus on the UK CSE, drawing on empirical data from their training and everyday work to examine some of their mundane practices. Paying particular attention to crime scene photography and crime scene reporting, I unpick

some of the expertise and sensory practices central to CSE work and explore how CSEs produce robust evidence by adopting specific ways of working that enable them to claim the objectivity of their labour. I show how the outputs of successful CSE work move seamlessly between different parts of the criminal justice system (Kruse 2020) and can also structure wider forensic practices and understandings of the crime itself. I end by reflecting on recent shifts in UK police forensic science to adopt national accreditation programmes and the implications of such programmes of standardisation for the CSE profession and meaningful CSE work at local and national levels.

Contests of Credibility: The Rise of At-home Rape Kits in the COVID Era *Andrea Quinlan, University of Waterloo*

At-home forensic rape kits have been marketed as a technoscientific solution to sexual violence. Specifically designed to allow sexual assault survivors to collect their own forensic evidence in the safety of their home, at-home rape kits have been cast by designers as an accessible and empowering alternative to hospital-based forensic exams. However, law enforcement agencies in the United States have been calling these kits 'dangerous' and challenging their legal credibility to identify sexual offenders and survivors' lack of expertise to use them. The COVID-19 pandemic has introduced a new urgency to these debates, amidst some evidence of declining numbers of survivors seeking hospital-based forensic exams. This paper examines the rise of at-home rape kits and the controversies over their use during the COVID-19 pandemic. The paper draws on 30 interviews with American victim advocates, forensic nurses, and lawyers, as well as a wealth of unobtrusive data, to explore what these controversies reveal about forensic expertise and credibility, and the growing tensions between do-it-yourself forensics and the law. Drawing on feminist and critical race STS scholarship, the paper considers how the marketing and controversies around at-home rape kits are fueling carceral logics and techno-optimism in forensics' power to prevent violent crime, and reflects on the broader implications for sexual assault prevention and anti-violence activism.

An STS ethnographic approach to Ecuador's prison massacre: how ultraviolet videos of riot killings became forensic evidence *Jorge Nunez, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*

In late February 2021, an unprecedented massacre took place in three different supermax prisons in Ecuador. 79 inmates were killed during a coordinated two-day prison riot staged in the cities of Latacunga, Cuenca, and Guayaquil. The killings were accompanied with extreme graphic violence in the form of gory cellphone videos filmed and circulated on social media by inmates. The footage is brutal: A heart beating on the hands of a prisoner laughing, a beheaded body lying on top of a pile of burnt corpses, and a group killing of a stripped-naked inmate in the prison courtyard. These videos are not completely new in the Ecuadorian context. They emerged in early 2019, when a video showing two inmates playing soccer with a decapitated head became trending topic on Twitter. At the time, the government declared a crisis in the prison system, deployed military troops to maximum-security penitentiaries across the country, and replaced public servants with police personnel. This presentation follows the forensic life of ultraviolet prison videos through police units, government institutions, and legal courts to question how the imagery of extreme violence translates into evidence-based knowledge. I pay particular attention to how police forensics worked on the massacre autopsies to certify the videos' authenticity, how government lawyers tried to make the videos inadmissible in court, and how human rights lawyers used the videos to obtain protection measures for inmates.

Session Organizers:

Dana Wilson-Kovacs, University of Exeter
David Wyatt, King's College London

Chair:

Dana Wilson-Kovacs, University of Exeter

187. Toxic Goodness: Harmful Legacies, Hopeful Futures – II

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

How do you cultivate good practices, relationships, and things in an environment of toxicants, toxic politics, and toxic relationalities? How do toxic production systems—based on extractivism, colonialism, and plantation capitalism—foment new forms of sustainability that cannot be excised from their deadly foundations? This open call examines urgent tensions between toxic legacies and hopeful futures when it comes to so-called renewable energies, green/blue/bio-economies, waste management systems, and sustainable agriculture/aquaculture. Such hopeful alternatives to unsustainable production systems hold within them the possibility of working towards a “Greater Good,” however, “goodness” is largely built on toxic colonial and capitalist foundations that are rendered invisible through sustainability discourse. In other words, in making sustainable things or practices, toxicities in many forms are in fact often sustained. This panel will therefore investigate the ways scientists, investors, and producers in the agricultural, aquacultural, and waste sectors build on toxic legacies as they seek to render generative material processes—such as photosynthesis, bioremediation, and fermentation—into sustainable tools. We encourage papers that empirically illuminate how social systems and material processes together shore up, generate, and maintain toxicity. Such investigations will open space to question whether and how good relations could be cultivated out of toxic relationships without assuming toxicity can be entirely expunged. The overall aim of this open panel is thus to critically address how sustainable processes depend on toxic production systems, as a first step towards activating better ways of living amid toxicity.

Participants:

Lesser Flamingo Life and Death: Nourishing Toxicity, ‘Generous’ Mines and Metabolic Transitions in Kimberley, South Africa *Carina Truys*, *Sol Plaatje University*

What makes a worthwhile object of care? Early in 2019 lesser Flamingo chick euphoria took hold of the small historical diamond mining city of Kimberley in central South Africa. A rapid, publicly driven rescue operation mobilized in response to the plight of thousands of baby flamingos, abandoned by their flock due to drought. Hundreds of volunteers streamed to the SPCA on the edge of the city where we cradled soft, quaking, chicks in our hands, tenderly forcing beaks open for syringes loaded with prawns and baby cereal, depleting these stocks from city supermarkets. The plight of the flamingoes was broadcast as far as the CNN, and donations solicited and sent from across the globe. Prominent among these was a local diamond mining company. The narrative around the plight of the chicks suggested the local municipality was to shoulder the blame for what was assumed to be a native flock crucial for species survival. However, the flock only settled there in 2005, and lesser flamingo regularly experience successive failed breeding seasons. Regarding municipal negligence, it was the most likely the very presence of effluent in water run-off that attracted them in the first instance due to its role in the production of nutritious algae. The same effluent is used in mining operations. This paper takes a cue from Hannah Landecker to “recount the remaking of nutritive and toxic relations between plants, animals, microbes, minerals and humans” (2019:551). Drawing on ethnography, interviews and media analysis I trace the value of sewerage in a complex web of care and value anchored in colonial and Apartheid norms of personhood. The analysis is scaled from minutiae (algae and mineral), across geological time, and geopolitical space (including Apartheid infrastructures, and bird and human guts). This metabolic approach conducted in the city famous for “the Big Hole” (the world’s largest open-pit mine) helps us glimpse the stakes in fashioning environments in the name of care.

An Extractive Science? Complicated Industries and Crude

Natures *Zsuzsanna Dominika Ihar*, *University of Sydney*

221 hectares of hydrocarbon-contaminated soil reimagined as a promissory garden bed. The renaturalisation and bioremediation of Qara Şəhər (Black City)—a historic industrial district of Baku, Azerbaijan—, was launched by state and corporate investors in 2011. The intended outcome of the ten-year project was the creation of Ağ Şəhər (White City), an eco-urban hybrid, which would signal the return of nature to a space that had been otherwise designated an unsalvageable wasteland. With the fast-paced demolition of petrochemical facilities, the introduction of biodiverse and exotic plant life, as well as the implementation of carbon neutral policies, state actors and environmental scientists alike celebrated the apparent liberation of the city from its toxic legacies – not only of crude oil contaminants, but also Soviet subjugation and widespread state corruption. Arguing against this neat narrative, the paper will make the case that, via processes of gentrification, the displacement of marginal communities, and the destruction of ruderal ecologies, remediation has actually continued the work of extractive capitalism in Baku. Furthermore, many of the greening projects have required the expertise and financial support of the oil industry, complicating the relationship between extractivism and environmentalism in both the capital city and the wider region of the Caucasus. Through examining collaborations between environmental scientists and oil corporations like SOCAR and BP, the paper will comment on the close entanglement between the extractive industry and scientific knowledge production. It will finish by pivoting towards local community practices –of backyard ‘neff’ gardens, seed care, and informal waste collection–, which seek to intercept the above-mentioned relationships and envision toxic land otherwise.

Beyond Remediation—Mourning as a New Worlding Practice *Caroline Ektander*, *Bauhaus Universität Weimar*

Bitterfeld—once known as the “dirtiest city in Europe”—is a post-industrial town and superfund site in former East Germany where processes of remediation have masked the legacies of industrialization through the spectacle of reconstructed nature and gentrification. Despite a booming chemical industry and investment in expensive technocentric measures to mitigate environmental violence over the past century—a task predicted to continue for at least the next 100 years—the regeneration of Bitterfeld remains partial and uneven. Many long-term effects of its industrial past and present on human and more-than-human societies are simply cast aside by current schemes. Using Bitterfeld as my case study, I intend to demonstrate how particular value systems and practices shape the remediation and regeneration of Bitterfeld—what it privileges and how—and what that says, more generally, about our permanently polluted world (Liboiron, et.al, 2018). Moreover, in order to move beyond remediation discourses and instead emphasize how the legacies of industrialization are a shared problem that require a radical re-imagining of relations of responsibility and collective care, my paper will introduce a design research methodology centered around loss and mourning. This will not only be a way to expand on the repertoire of remediation by acknowledging lost and severed relations between different concerned publics and the land but also as a strategy to stimulate public encounters that seek to establish new bonds.

Caring For and Living With Extractive Legacies in Northern Canada *Caitlynn Beckett*, *Memorial University of Newfoundland*, *Department of*

The closure and waste management phases of a mine’s lifecycle have complex socio-economic and cultural impacts on local communities. Yet, the ongoing community care dimensions of these waste landscapes typically receive less attention than engineered containment solutions. Remediation projects have the potential to further entrench environmental injustices, land dispossession and colonial environmental management

techniques under the guise of 're-greening'. In this sense, the remedial process of making contaminated landscapes 'better' results in the perpetuation of colonial extraction long after a mine has closed. Drawing inspiration from community interventions in mine remediation projects across Northern Canada, this research challenges normative definitions of remediation, explores anti-colonial remedial practices, and evaluates how environmental regulations address (or fail to address) the layered complexities of healing land. I have partnered with the Ross River Dena Council (RRDC), whose unceded territory has been drastically impacted by the now abandoned, lead-zinc Faro Mine. RRDC wants to ensure that the Faro Remediation Project brings safety and economic benefits to their community, but they are also focused on healing the legacies of the past, reclaiming dispossessed land and asserting self-determination for the future. With these community objectives in mind, interviews, archival analysis, literature reviews, and participatory action research are being used to stitch together multiple methods for community-centered remediation. Such methods are relevant to resisting colonial extractivism and providing a more robust understanding of how to ethically manage waste in order to develop better, albeit messy, mechanisms for living in/with post-industrial landscapes.

Rethinking Plastic Realities: A Call for a Well-being Approach to Understanding Human-plastic Entanglements *Jessica Vandenberg, University of Washington; marlena skrobe; Jill Fallman, University of Washington; Karin Otsuka, University of Washington; Ivy Serwaa Gyimah Akuoko, University of Cape Coast; Suzy An, University of Washington*

Plastics have emerged as the omnipresent material and challenge of the Anthropocene. Since the mid 20th century, a staggering amount of plastics have been produced, manufactured, used, disposed of and accumulated as waste in the environment. Despite their benefits, plastics are threatening the health and well-being of human and non-human life forms (Alkire 2002; Sangha et al. 2015; Sen 1993; 1999). While the plastics crisis is documented, there is little understanding of the dynamic lived experiences of coastal communities disrupted by plastic waste. Moreover, there is a need for understanding the social life of plastics and how they impact well-being across their many life stages. This study explores human-plastic entanglements, asking how colonial and toxic legacies, issues of inequity, and well-being are embedded into the social life of plastics and the ways plastics are managed and mismanaged. To address these questions we implemented a co-produced survey in a small community in Elmina, Ghana where locals are highly dependent upon their surrounding coastal environment and plastic waste entanglements are of serious concern. Beyond this initial study, the survey instrument can serve as a more holistic guide for future assessments of the role of plastics in communities and the ways in which local people can inform equitable and locally-appropriate mitigation solutions.

Session Organizers:

Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University
Jessica Caporusso, York University
Katie Ulrich, Rice University

Chair:

Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University

Discussant:

Timothy Neale, Deakin University

188. Relations and Troubles of Tools of Valuation – V

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

The economics of climate futures: mitigation pathways as tools

of valuation *Béatrice Cointe, CNRS*

Quantified scenarios and pathways are ubiquitous in discussions on climate change. As tools to perform certain futures and possibilities, but also to stress what needs to change now, they have taken an eminently political character. One prominent type of scenarios are those projecting the evolution of greenhouse gas emissions and climate policy options. Most of the time we encounter these as graphs displaying an array of "roads-yet-to-be-taken", but they are in fact complex sets of interrelated numerical variables produced by models – specifically, Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs) – and collected in databases. This presentation will analyse such scenarios, and the models that are used to produce them, as tools of ordering and valuation by interrogating the practices and infrastructures that make them work. To do so, it will focus on the way categories and valuation practices from economics have been incorporated in the climate scenario production infrastructure, and have come to be debated as a result. IAMs indeed rely on economics-based conceptions of change and decision-making, especially regarding innovation and growth. Ongoing debates on negative emissions, on the likelihood of worst-case scenarios, or on the possibility of economic growth in a changing climate, are putting the spotlight on the economic valuations embedded in IAM scenarios and on their role in shaping climate (in)action. I will ask: How do the scenarios produced by IAMs, together with the infrastructure of scenario-production, perform specific conceptions of innovation and growth? How does this shape the climate futures deemed possible or likely, and with what political consequences?

Re-valuing Oil: Tracing The Shifting Regimes and 'Tools of Valuation' in The Governing of the Norwegian Oil Economy *Kristin Asdal, TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture; Bård Lahn, CICERO Center for International Climate Research Oslo*

How do valuation practices and practices of governing go together? And how do the tools of valuation involved work upon the very objects and issues in question? In oil-rich Norway, valuing oil is not confined to market operations. It is also a key aspect of governmental practices to manage and control the oil economy. As new global climate targets have made fossil fuel production increasingly contested, discussions about the future of oil have become closely linked to a specific financialized way of valuing oil resources. This paper shows how the valuation of Norwegian oil has shifted over the last half-century. While in the 1970s oil was valued in terms of the industrial activity it would generate, from the late 1980s it was increasingly valued as an 'asset', based on the present worth of expected future revenue. The paper explores the implications of new valuation practices for the governing of oil, as well as for current political controversies about its future in a world moving away from fossil fuels. Analytically, we follow the 'tools of valuation' involved in governing oil as they move across markets and government. Our analysis highlights the need for studying practices and regimes of valuations in ways that are able to capture how objects such as oil gain their worth not only at the market, but in politics and administration as well. Thus, the paper argues that we need to relate not just to market devices, but to valuations more broadly. Hence, the notion 'tools of valuations'.

Déjà Vu? The Troubles of Valuing and Verifying Carbon Offsetting in the Global North *Kamilla Karhunmaa, University of Helsinki*

Declarations of "carbon neutrality by 2035 or 2050" have become daily features in our lives, present in food packages and news headlines. At the same time, carbon neutrality remains an interpretatively flexible term that leaves particularly the role of offsetting opaque. While voluntary carbon offset projects are located primarily in the Global South, increased societal pledges to become "carbon neutral" have led to developing offset projects in the Global North too. In this presentation, I examine how new

offset providers in Finland tackle the tensions and troubles of valuing carbon and verifying emissions reductions. Finland currently exhibits over a dozen new initiatives that seek to provide voluntary offsets through land-use and forestry projects. These projects are emerging in a landscape of climate action that is both adamant on announcing emissions reductions and critical of several of the previous practices of voluntary offsetting. This has led to a mixed situation where some actors are pursuing verification through existing standards, others are seeking to develop new types of emissions reductions certificates, many are failing to verify emissions reductions and others are seeking to distance themselves from the language of selling emissions reductions altogether. The tension of creating standardized units that nonetheless should be somehow differentiated from other offset units seems to be re-emerging. Meanwhile, the lack of institutionalized approaches, the plethora of available options and the uncertain relation to other policies, such as the Paris Agreement, means that governing voluntary offsets in the North is very much in the making.

Fossil Free Futures: enabling socially responsible investments in pension funds *Linda Soneryd S*

Phasing out fossil fuels is increasingly viewed as a competitive advantage rather than a necessary cost to combat climate change. Nevertheless, large amounts of money are still channelled to fossil fuel extracting activities, also in the context of state-managed pension funds. Fossil free investments are increasingly attended to in relation to the pension funds and many new initiatives to divest the funds have emerged. In this paper the actors, tools and valuation practices involved in divesting the pension funds are explored. Empirically the paper focus on an activist company that has developed an app to display information about the content of investments to individual savers. What information is gathered and displayed? What are the valuation practices involved in shaping this tool? How can users interact with the app, and what are their responses? Conceptually the paper discusses pension savings as an inherently ambivalent issue, involving tensions between expectations of high investment returns, as well as ethical concerns around what activities are invested in, and how these may contribute to futures that are undesirable. The paper discusses how tools aiming to guide individual pension savers in socially responsible investments, may themselves become new sources of ambivalence.

Valuing and devaluing goods for sustainability. The case of energy labels for buildings in France *Alexandre Mallard, Centre de Sociologie de l'Innovation-i3 – Mines Paristech PSL University; Catherine Grandclément, EDF R&D*

In 2002, a European directive extended energy labels, previously used for light bulbs and household appliances, to the real estate market. Called 'Energy Performance Certificates' (EPC), energy labels for buildings measure and rank dwellings on an A to G (green to red) scale according to their energy performance. In France today, EPCs are used as a steering device of buildings sustainability. Some of its most notable uses are to equip buyers' cognition, to signal dwellings that are open to subsidies for energy retrofit and to define targets for the 'greening' policy of the housing stock. A current revision of EPC in France offers a crucial venue to question the links between energy performance calculation and associated forms of valuation. The revision, intended to increase the reliability of EPCs, has also modified the calculation methods, shattering the previous ranking of dwellings and the market. Previously badly rated dwellings that may have been discarded by reasonable buyers and investors and were priority targets for energy retrofit will now receive decent grades while other dwellings which were preferred by those same sound buyers and investors are now declared low-quality. Another controversial outcome of the changed ranking scale is the planned prohibition from 2028 onwards of bottom-of-scale properties (called 'energy sieves')

from the sale and renting markets. Based on a study of the technical controversies and political debates surrounding the calculation of the new EPC and its consequences, the paper will explore the logic of a mode of government in which an ordering device is used to decrease the economic value of properties considered politically undesirable.

Drawing the line: Opening up and closing down the siting of a high voltage transmission route in the Netherlands *Udo Pesch, Delft University of Technology; Toyah Rodhouse, Delft University of Technology; Shannon Spruit, Delft University of Technology; Antje Ten Haaf, Dialoogisch; Jochem Dijkshoorn, WB de Ruimte*

This paper describes the decision-making process regarding the siting of a high voltage transmission line in the southern part of the Netherlands by TenneT, which is the organization responsible for the maintenance, operation and development of electricity infrastructure in the Netherlands and Germany. TenneT started this siting process by deploying conventional decision-making procedures and valuation tools, which have the tendency to centrally pre-scope, select the technical, spatial and societal characteristics of such projects. Due to the resistance of activist groups and local authorities, a new siting process was set up based on the upfront inclusion of local stakeholders so to include new frames and perspectives and by reconsidering the workings of standard procedures and valuation tools. Most notably, the normativities and political connotations of the compulsory environmental assessment report were taken as reflective input for the process. As such, TenneT can be said to have aspired the 'opening up' of decision-making processes. In our paper, we will identify the practical and institutional tensions and challenges that emerged from these attempts to 'open up', and more particularly look at the functioning of institutionalized valuation tools. Our paper analysis is based on an 'inside out' description of the case: one of the researchers has made an ethnographic study of the siting process; and the employees of TenneT directly involved in the siting process have been invited as co-authors, so details and the reflections of practitioners could be added.

Session Organizers:

Kristin Asdal, TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture

Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech

Chair:

Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna

189. Aerotechnologies: Air as Elemental Technology - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

"Objects, processes, or events that in some ways disclose, generate, or intensify the condition of being enveloped by the elemental force of atmospheres," Derek McCormack (2018) proposes, are "atmospheric things." The balloon, for instance, might be construed as a device that not only explicates but also draws force from its immersion in air. We invite papers that contend with aerotechnologies, understood as infrastructures, devices, knowledge systems, and particles that make air as such a technological fact as it is a natural one. What does it mean to study air as elemental technology? How is air — as an element — constitutive, pervasive, and facilitative of emergent kinds of social experiences and relations? How are wind (Howe 2019, Boyer 2019), climate engineering (Furuhata 2019), teargas (Nieuwenhuis 2016), industrial gases (Banken and Stokes 2015), terrariums (Darby 2007), breathing (Braun 2014; Mbembe 2020), as well as other airy matters technologically mediated, rendered, and configured? How does air come to be known or contested through processes of racial, (settler) colonial, and capitalist formations (Flikke 2018, Simmons 2017)? If *techné* denotes the practices of making, we propose that aerotechnologies relate and relay connections between people, non-human actors, epochs, and places, evoking the conference theme that asks what are good (airy) relations? In addition to treating air as technological, we are also interested in papers that explore air as an

elemental medium that link different scales of political and social action (Peters 2015, Horn 2018, Choy 2011), especially from perspectives tethered in the global South.

Participants:

Forensic Dustups, Smokestacks, and a Toxic Breeze *Julia Huggins, Brown University*

The axiom of forensic science—‘every contact leaves a trace’—derives from French criminologist Edmond Locard’s work on dust evidence. Locard asserted that “the microscopic debris that cover our clothes and bodies are the mute witnesses, sure and faithful, of all our movements and of all our encounters.” Locard rendered dust as a kind of evidence of contagion. Alongside the development of the crime scene in the 19th century, dust emerged as the forensic object par excellence. Dust is either made material, measurable, and manageable. Yet what remains under-interrogated about dust in the forensic imagination is its fugitivity, its viral movement through the air. If contagion highlights connectivity, what, then, does dust do? I argue that dust offers a way of thinking air as technological. Early theories of dust traces wed networks of connection to culpability – a factory worker’s route home through industrial city blocks produced the residue that would incriminate him (as opposed to the evidence of the structural violences of capitalism). What happens when we attend to dust not at its destination (in a coat pocket), but in its mode of travel, its atmospheric dispersion? This paper demonstrates how, instead of individualizing culpability, dust might be enlisted into a counter-forensic project. I analyze environmental justice efforts around sites such as the ASARCO smokestacks of El Paso and the toxic mining pit in Butte, Montana. What if dust were to be taken seriously as evidence of the culpability of the network itself and the interests it serves?

From Road Warrior to Digital Nomad: Portability, Atmospheres, and the Engineering of the World *Renyi Hong, National University of Singapore (NUS)*

Although “portability” is often deployed to reference mobile technologies, its use in software engineering communicates a quality of environmental adaptability. This article enters from this vantage to emphasize the vertical, atmospheric, and habitual cultural logic of portable computers. Following the terms “road warrior” to “digital nomad,” it examines how portability has served an imperialist function in engineering a world fit for buffering privileged subjects against conditions of existential precariousness. The story begins in the air: road warriors of the 80s and 90s had used the challenges of airplane environments to legitimate their superior capacities to adapt to the difficulties of working in flight. Portable computers made salient the ways that atmospheres differentially disposed towards work subjects, which also supported the claim of adaptive superiority that road warriors expressed. Set against a period of rising precariousness in middle-management, such claims of environmental adaption was able to reinforce the corporate value of road warriors. This story will change by the late 90s as infrastructures became more accommodating. This time, the standardization of environments would prompt an imaginary of redistribution, where problems of the global North are shifted to the Global South. Digital nomads enact this history today when they relate how standardized Wi-Fi atmospheres had enabled them to adapt at scale, to cobble a good life in third-world countries with an unstable income, linking atmospheric adaptability again with racial privilege. This argument draws from historical computing magazines and newspapers, and interviews and fieldwork conducted in Bali and Chiang Mai.

Masking Plagues: 'Airborne' Disease and the Science, Politics and Design of Medical Facemasks *Lyle Fearnley, Singapore University of Technology and Design*

During the Covid-19 pandemic, billions of people began to wear face masks in an unprecedented global public health campaign.

In many places, however, ‘masking up’ was controversial: protests broke out against “mask slavery,” and scientists disagreed about the efficacy of masks. This paper draws on historical and anthropological research to trace the intersections between the science of airborne disease, the technical design of facemasks, and the adoption, transformation or rejection of masks by the wider public. After the germ theory’s displacement of the epistemology of miasma—or ‘bad air’—as a cause of disease, medical consensus about ‘airborne’ disease remained elusive. Today, disputes continue between aerosol specialists and medical doctors around the definition of ‘airborne’ vs. ‘droplet’ infection and their role in disease transmission. When facemasks are designed and used for epidemic control, therefore, they function as ‘aerotechnologies’ that materialize theories about airborne transmission, often in the absence of experimental evidence. Further, the face mask is also a semiotic device—a garment that participates in a broader cultural practice of dress—whose public meanings exceed their scientific and medical function, particularly because of the cultural and political meanings associated with breath, face, speech, air, and atmosphere. Drawing on interviews with aerosol researchers, medical doctors, mask designers, mask users and anti-mask protesters, primarily in Singapore and the United States, this paper examines the face mask as a device through which relations among bodies, and between bodies and atmospheres, are being remade.

Session Organizer:

Jia Hui Lee, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Chair:

Boyd Ruamcharoen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Discussant:

Lyle Fearnley, Singapore University of Technology and Design

190. Contemplating Models and Methods for Futures in-the-making - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Predicting and planning for the future is an inherently uncertain exercise. In the midst of unfolding health and environmental crises, forecasting the implications of different types of interventions is important but precarious. With exhortations from governments to ‘flatten the curve,’ simulation modelling has recently gained prominence in public consciousness as a potent tool informing COVID policies. The simplicity of the models stands in stark contrast to the complexity of the challenges at hand. This panel explores ways for STS to interpret and inform debates around ‘modelling’ practice and public understandings of models for the future. How and why are simulation models so seductive? How are models shaping concepts of ‘self’ and ‘future’? What kinds of knowledges and assumptions are built into these speculative exercises and what (or who) is left out? Can models help build ‘good relations’ between governments and citizens, or between diverse stakeholders approaching complex problems? The panel invites papers that engage with critical approaches to modelling practice and models as symbols circulating in complex systems. We also encourage papers that explore alternative methods for engaging in forecasting and scenario building that may better be able to encompass complex intervention dynamics and marginalized futures.

Participants:

Models as Viral Assemblages *Marit Ostebo, University of Florida*

Scholars situated within critical policy studies and anthropology have, in recent years, paid considerable attention to the model as a traveling phenomenon. Inspired by assemblage thinking and Science and Technology Studies, the existing literature provide nuanced perspectives on what facilitates the circulation of models. There has been limited attention to why a particular model or idea gains its status and starts traveling in the first place, however. What is it that makes a model attractive? Why do

some models go viral, why others do not? In this paper I use the example of Awra Amba, a rural village in Northern Ethiopia that has become a model for gender equality and sustainable development, to further the existing scholarship on traveling models. Inspired by assemblage thinking, Gabriel Tarde's social epidemiology, and virology I argue that a traveling model can best be understood as a viral assemblage – here dually defined as a messy, fluid, socio-technical process and a constellation of actors, unpredictable events and relations that have contagious and affective qualities. Just as for a virus, the model's travel and its contagious capacity are conditioned on vectors, hospitable environments, and receptive host cells. For a model to spread, there needs to be an association or element of recognition and interaction between the model and the entities that may connect with it. These associations tend to be affective in character. Looking at models through the lens of viral assemblage implies attention to how affect is both constitutive of the model and derived from it.

Open Science or Closed Circuits of Expertise? Modelling Different Futures *Catharina Landström, Chalmers University of Technology*

Digital technologies have the potential to make scientific knowledge, data and tools available to all at low cost. Bundled together under the notion of Open Science visions include the publication of data and evidence that can be used to plan activities across many fields. Other ideas are to make analytical tools available to everybody facilitating the reproduction and quality control of research findings. Further, scientific computer models are used to create decision support tools for use by a variety of societal actors. In addition, digital technologies enable interested lay people to get involved with scientific research in citizen science. Open Science has the potential to firmly establish science as a public good. However, it takes no stretch of the imagination to think that things could turn out differently. In addition to the well-known digital divide that marginalises those without access to the hardware, there is also a risk that the need for computer modelling skills combined with disciplinary knowledge will prompt the development of new expertise that marginalises other ways of generating knowledge. Such tendencies can currently be identified in environmental research where computer simulation modelling is becoming the favoured approach among scientists, funding bodies and some private businesses. It appears that problems and knowledge not conducive to computational analysis attract less interest and funding regardless of their 'real-world' importance. Drawing on water management modelling this paper reflects on the challenges such closed circuits of expertise pose to the realisation of open science.

Pandemic models in popular media: plotting alternative futures *Ana Maria Borlescu, University of Bucharest; Ana Cosima Rughinis, University of Bucharest*

The COVID-19 pandemic has led to an increase in uncertainty in many realms of social life. This led the general public and decision makers alike to turn to expert knowledge of the past and present, in an attempt to plot the ongoing crisis and post-pandemic trajectories. Epidemiological and infection models are pieces of scientific knowledge often reported on by mass-media, informing public debates and policy decisions, and quantifying (Espeland and Stevens, 2008) alternative social trajectories. Models are used as argumentative devices in popular media articles, enabling commensuration of heterogeneous activities (Espeland and Stevens, 1998), comparisons, and predictions about the evolution of the COVID-19 pandemic. They also enact a discursive construction of temporality, through time work (Flaherty, 2003), shaping readers' definitions of the situation and anticipations of post-pandemic recovery. How are pandemic models represented in popular media? How have these representations changed over the course of the COVID-19 pandemic? How do models construct the pandemic timeline and,

consequently, project social activities? How is present-day knowledge used in models to imagine future developments in a post-pandemic society? Our paper analyses a broad collection of journal articles that work on pandemic temporalities, focusing on a subset of articles which reference pandemic models from two Anglo-American daily newspapers, The New York Times and The Guardian, published over the first year of the COVID-19 pandemic (January 2020 - January 2021), to identify the role of quantification and commensuration in charting possible futures.

Qualitative Quagmires. Risk preparation with Bayesian Networks and causal mapping *Tapio Reinekoski, Tampere University; Marko Ahvenainen, University of Turku; Nina Janasik, University of Helsinki; Annukka Lehtikoinen, University of Helsinki*

We present a concept for a simulation exercise of risk preparedness and a case study of its first application with public official experts of a Finnish city. The exercise begins with a narrative disaster scenario of an industrial logistics accident and a chemical spill. The acute ramifications are represented with a Bayesian Network model, whose causal logic the participants will follow as they deliberate on the future causal mechanisms and mediating factors that could endanger the city's long-term strategic goals. After the designers code the discussions into an extended, calculable model, the participants can experiment with the system and tease out the most critical risks in the model's causal network. For the analysis of both the exercise and its design process, we appropriate the concept of qualcalculation (Cochoy, 2002, 2008) to examine how the exercise elicits 'separate but mutually constitutive' (Callon & Law, 2005) considerations of and translations between quantitative information and qualitative judgment. We follow the participants as they negotiate social, economic, and political assessments with numerical probabilities and causalities to gain actionable foresight. The design and implementation deserve similar scrutiny, for example, when numerically representing participants' insights on the qualities of causal connections. Resolving such qualitative quagmires remains insolubly partial, but can, we suggest, inject a critical outlook into the design of techniques of preparing (for) future risks. Bayesian causal modelling seems to suit this purpose as it evokes the enactment of probabilities together with the underlying qualitative assumptions of what is possible and plausible.

Socialising Models: From Life Stories to Population Models of Disease *Victoria Loblay, Menzies Centre for Health Policy, The Australian Prevention Partnership Centre*

Dynamic simulation models are becoming increasingly important tools for health policy decision-making. Through the COVID-19 pandemic, we have seen how models have been instrumental in transforming conceptions of expertise. There is growing awareness and desire to engage with 'evidence': to have input into it, to make it and translate it (Rhodes et al. 2020). This paper explores the sociality of models and modelling practices designed to simulate disease prevention and inform health policy. The 'social' is considered from two angles. Firstly, model building is explored as a collaborative practice, a form of co-production which builds 'good relations' (or otherwise) between researchers, policymakers, experts and citizens. With the proliferation of participatory modelling methods, who is participating in making models, and who is left out? Secondly, the paper explores how 'evidence' is socialised and brought to life in modelling practice. It considers how storytelling features in the making and movement of models and what kinds of knowledge are valued as evidence in the process. As modelling practices gain increasing prominence, bringing an STS perspective to examine models and their sociality is important to enable a better understanding of the multiple roles of participatory simulation modelling within complex systems and the value of engaging with modelling processes. Rhodes, T.,

Lancaster, K., & Rosengarten, M. (2020) A model society: maths, models and expertise in viral outbreaks, *Critical Public Health*, 30:3, 253-256

Session Organizer:

Victoria Loblay, Menzies Centre for Health Policy, The Australian Prevention Partnership Centre

191. Making and Doing Exhibit

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: Making and Doing

Making and Doing Exhibit

Participant:

Making and Doing Exhibit *Hélène Mialet, York University STS*
Making and Doing Exhibit

Session Organizer:

Hélène Mialet, York University STS

192. Epistemic Infrastructures - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Participants:

“Fending off the Donor”: Statistical Capacity Development and Measuring Epistemic Infrastructures *Marlee Tichenor, University of Edinburgh*

Designating statistical capacity development (SCD) as a target for measurement in the Sustainable Development Goals created a dilemma for statistical decision-makers in the United Nations system. Some statisticians saw the inclusion of statistical capacity in SDG17 as a ‘conflict of interest’, making their work both a beneficiary of the SDGs and a means to achieve them. The three indicators for SCD in individual countries are: (1) levels of funding, (2) the existence of a National Strategy for the Development of Statistics, and (3) the existence of statistical legislation. In this article, I argue that the infrastructuralisation of statistical capacity as a development problem into the SDG framework provides a unique lens into the epistemic infrastructure of the agenda as a whole: its materialities and actors, its networks and processes, and its global public policy. Like all indicators in the SDG framework, statistical capacity indicators are performative, defined and delineated by the global statistics community which also defines and delineates development problem to be addressed. Unlike other indicators, however, statistical capacity indicators have an added weight of also producing the conditions of possibility for the global public policy agenda as a whole. In this way, control over its measurement is particularly important, as it will determine what will be possible on both the national and global level for the coming decade and beyond.

Forging Care: health cards, indicators, and global governance in Tanzania *Megan Cogburn, University of Florida*

Over the last two decades, there has been a global push to improve pregnancy and childbirth care by improving key antenatal and delivery indicators. While recent scholarship has interrogated the increasing hegemony of metrics in global health, few have ethnographically explored how this push for numbers and its accompanying technologies affect the lived experiences of mothers and those who care for them on the ground in rural communities. Based on eight months of ethnographic research conducted in rural Tanzania in 2019, this paper explores the suspicions, accusations, and rumors surrounding the forging of prenatal and child health cards, key actants of national health governance, surveillance, and care. I show how mothers and health workers used health card forgeries as a way to make sense of, question, and bypass indicator-driven policies and sanctions that do not reflect their lived experiences or desires. Health card forgeries became central to “forging care”—the complex process of creating new caring relations and possibilities. I push this

concept of “forging care” further to show how the object of the forged health card becomes a larger symbol of the authentic-fake nature of what counts as care in global ‘epistemic care infrastructures’ dependent on numbers. For what counts as care is that which can be documented—that which can be quantified and measured, and also in new, creative ways, be forged.

How the science of HIV treatment-as-prevention restructured PEPFAR’s strategy *Ryan Whitacre, IHEID*

The clinical logics of HIV treatment-as-prevention structured PEPFAR’s latest strategic initiative to achieve ‘epidemic control’ including the organisation’s use of metrics for evaluating performance, and decisions for allocating funds to specific programs and countries. TasP was initially conceptualised as an ‘evidence-based’ solution for effectively treating and preventing HIV, which could be consistently measured and reported on, however its ability to produce the right kinds of evidence remained abstract and hypothetical. Nevertheless, PEPFAR relied on these metrics to make big claims about its own impact on the epidemic. The effects of TasP have also been evident in the budget since PEPFAR launched the strategy to achieve ‘epidemic control’. Whereas under previous initiatives to ‘lead to the global response’ to the epidemic, PEPFAR supported a wider variety of program areas, including by strengthening health systems, under the strategy of epidemic control PEPFAR has prioritised treatment programs over and above all others. TasP also justified disproportionate spending on a subset of countries. While this subset of 13 countries has received significantly more support since the initiative began, long-term trends in the budget also reveal that PEPFAR has prioritised these countries since its establishment as an organisation. By adopting the clinical logics of TasP, PEPFAR justified spending on a limited number of programmes in a small set of countries that could produce what it defined as the right kinds of outcomes, and laid the groundwork for the retreat of US foreign aid. However, PEPFAR must now reckon with the blind spot of an overly biomedical approach, and answer difficult questions about who, and what, has and will be left behind.

The Privatization of Metrics in the Pandemic Response *Katerini T Storeng, University of Oslo*

This panel considers how quantification in global governance can be seen as an ‘epistemic infrastructure’ that is embedded in structures, technologies and social arrangements. I argue that the Covid-19 pandemic has revealed that this ‘epistemic infrastructure’ is increasingly privately owned, creating barriers to public authorities’ ability to mount an effective response as well as to public accountability. I develop this argument through three examples. First, pharmaceutical companies restrict access to ‘proprietary’ metrics on Covid-19 products’ efficacy, production costs, prices and profit margins, and supply capacity, and even give privileged vaccine access to countries willing to hand over citizen’s metrics (as Pfizer has done with Israel). Second, social media and telecommunication companies own and control access to data about human mobility public authorities need to model the pandemic’s course and to assess social countermeasures. Third, Big Tech companies Apple and Google own the exposure notification technology behind digital contact tracing apps and, on privacy grounds, restrict authorities’ access to the user data needed to integrate digital and manual contact tracing and to assess the cost-effectiveness of digital contact tracing. Such practices mean that publics everywhere must rely on uncertain estimates, projections and leaks to hold public authorities to account. Pharma companies’ lack of transparency about key metrics is particularly pernicious, undermining coordinated equitable global distribution of medicines and vaccines, and encouraging hoarding and vaccine nationalism. In conclusion, I consider long-term consequences of the ongoing privatisation of global ‘epistemic infrastructure’ for the balance of public and private power in public health governance.

Accounting for the European Union. Harmonization and

tensions around the measurement of the national economy. *Quentin Dufour, CNRS - I3 - CSI, Mines ParisTech*

Since the 1990s, the European Union has been monitoring the public finances of its member states. In order to know and intervene on national budgets, it relies on debt and deficit ratios derived from national accounts, the main epistemic infrastructure on the economy. Traditionally shaped for macroeconomic regulation, the use of national accounts to evaluate deficit levels implies a harmonization of accounting categories at the European level. Nevertheless these harmonization efforts create problems in the quantification practices of national statistical institutes, and complicate the ability of member states to produce a representation of the economy. Drawing on STS and the sociology of quantification, this presentation looks at the effects of accounting harmonization on the measurement of the economy. How are European accounting requirements transforming the way national economies are quantified? My analysis is based on my PhD thesis work on the construction of national accounts in the French case. I conducted a nine-month ethnographic fieldwork within the French administration in charge of quantifying the national economy - the National Accounts Department, within the French statistical institute (INSEE). I show that the stability of the epistemic infrastructure of the economy is not just a problem of accounting categories: despite a common accounting framework, French and European statisticians disagree on how to quantify, and produce different, even competing, representations of the economy.

Session Organizer:

Marlee Tichenor, University of Edinburgh

Chair:

Justyna Bandola-Gill, University of Edinburgh

193. Collective Organizing in the Face of Automation: Invisible work, Artificial Intelligence, and the gig economy.

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

The nature of 'going to work' is changing in fundamental ways. First, AI-driven automation has the potential to displace increasingly-broad sets of roles, including an expansion into and beyond service roles traditionally performed by humans. Further, issues raised among research into the growing gig economy have brought to the fore the potential for unfair treatment and unjust employment dynamics among those undertaking short-term, self-directed work. Finally, workers possess, to an increasing degree, the necessary skills and expertise to automate significant portions of their own work, threatening their job stability and leading to what might be thought of as 'self-obsolescence'. These workers may be newly or imminently displaced by novel implementations of AI, may find the circumstances of their work life to be substantially changed, or may have to operate under the often under-negotiated and under-secure conditions of the gig economy. Today, during what is perhaps the most dramatic period of growth in remote work, there is a growing need to closely examine collective organizing as job roles, daily practice, and even demographics shift alongside mediating technologies. With an eye toward the future of work, it is of pressing importance to consider whether the basic practices and roles of collective organizing still apply, or if they might need significant readjustment.

Participants:

A Dribbble Investigation: Making visible the labor of design
Yiran Duan, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University; Jeff Hemsley, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University; Rebecca D Kelly, Assistant Professor

This research seeks to investigate how designers (e.g. UX/UI, graphic, illustrators and others) on the website Dribbble.com, a niche platform created in 2009 for designers to share and get feedback on their work, and how users see sites like Dribbble impacting the design industry. As a platform which offers abundant resources for designers to look for inspiration and work opportunities, Dribbble.com interested our research team with its

potential to impact the design industry. The research team conducted 30 semi-structured interviews with designers who are active on Dribbble around the world. The interview data shows that although Dribbble provides work and networking opportunities for freelance designers, the scale of the site creates an expectation among clients that design work is cheap. This view devalues the designers' skills and therefore threatens job stability in the industry. The norm on Dribbble is for designers to post final products instead of the design process. This makes the labor of design invisible to would be clients. The research team offers website design prescriptions to expose the labor in ways that should increase awareness around the effort of design in the hope that the value can be perceived. The work also contributes to the growing literature around invisible labor.

Hidden Humans in the Loop: Unpacking Societal Challenges in the Curation of Facial Recognition Datasets *Benedetta Catanzariti, Science, Technology and Innovation Studies, The University of Edinburgh; Sarah Bennett, University of Edinburgh*

Over the last decade, applications of AI facial recognition have been implemented in a wide range of sensitive domains. These applications are often predicated upon machine learning algorithms trained on large-scale datasets consisting of labelled images categorised according to specific, pre-selected features. Many commercial facial recognition algorithms are trained on datasets whose images are labelled by crowdsourced workers, such as Amazon's Mechanical Turkers. The proposed paper reflects on a series of online participatory workshops with AI practitioners which explored the real-world practice of data curation work and examined the contexts within which much of facial recognition dataset labelling occurs, how they potentially impact the pipelines and outcomes of facial recognition systems, and the agency of individual workers within crowd-sourcing approaches. Moving beyond evaluation of forms of technical accuracy or 'de-biasing' datasets, our aim is to foster critical understandings of the value-laden decisions which are made by human labellers that lead to certain classifications. In doing so, we promote insight into the working practices, challenges and constraints faced by human labellers that are often outside the purview of AI practitioners, and thus critical reflection into their own practices. Building on literature around crowdsourced data work, this paper challenges dominant narratives on automation by centering the invisible labor behind the functioning of many AI technologies and, considering growing critiques of power asymmetries in the design of AI technologies, explores methods for the creation of more participatory and democratic AI systems. Paper co-authored with Sarah Bennett (Edinburgh College of Art, University of Edinburgh), sarah.bennett@ed.ac.uk

Session Organizer:

Stephen Slota, The University of Texas at Austin

194. Crip/STS Convergences In Transplantation Technologies: Critical Methods For The Curative Imaginary

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Often considered a pinnacle of medical technoscience, solid organ transplantation and related interventional devices (ventricular assist devices, VADs; extracorporeal membrane oxygenation, ECMO) are described and hoped for as a new and improved state that achieves or approximates cure from serious end-organ disease. At the same time, notions of cure and biomedicine's "curative imaginary" (Kafer 2013; Clare 2017) have come increasingly under scrutiny as hegemonic ways of knowing and experiencing futurities where health is seen as limitless and intervention inevitable. This open panel asks, "what futures materialize, when transplant medicine is brought into conversation with a critical stance that questions presuppositions about life, livability, difference, and thriving?" We invite those working at critical intersections in STS, particularly critical disability ("crip") studies and feminist STS, to bring their practices and methods to bear on the field of transplantation as well as

transplant-related technologies and sciences. We are especially interested in papers that reflect on futurity as an unstable horizon that requires innovation in methods and practices—from arts-based methods and research creation, to sound studies, to social geographies, to ethnography—how might a diversity of approaches in STS help to understand issues such as the liminality of being waitlisted, the challenges of adhering to strict regimens to preserve a transplanted organ, or the not-infrequent experience of graft rejection? We welcome a range of formats for presentation and will work with presenters to ensure that their work is accessible. The panel will be graphically recorded as part of a larger knowledge mobilization practice.

Participants:

“See You On The DIEP Side”: Cancer Time, Flap Transplants, Transfeminisms, and Crip Feminist STS *Evangeline (Vange) Heiliger, Smith College American Studies*

This paper engages feminist STS, transfeminisms, and crip theory to query unstable cancer time with DIEP flap breast reconstruction surgeries that promise “wholeness” to women- and femme-identified breast cancer patients through the use of transplantation technologies. Using ethnographic research from breast cancer patients, and drawing on E. Hayward’s “Lessons from a Starfish” and Clare’s and Kafer’s understandings of “curative imaginary,” and Ehler’s feminist STS elaboration on the “tekhne of cancer,” I draw out tensions between DIEP flap (and other flap surgeries) as potentially life-affirming gender confirmation—yet simultaneously promising an impossible dream: that of “moving beyond” cancer time into a post-cancer body and life free of disease, discomfort and pain. I argue that patient discourses around DIEP flap breast reconstructions, flap failures, breast revisions, and post-surgery healing come to mark moments within cancer time, rather than an end point that marks a body healed from breast cancer.

The Drift of the “Gift of Life”: Biocapital and the Practices of Marginal Kidney Transplantation in China *FAN ZHOU, Tsinghua University; Yongguang Liu, Zhujiang Hospital Affiliated to Southern Medical University; Pusheng Wang, Tsinghua University*

Marginal donors have increasingly become the choice for hospitals and some transplant recipients due to the huge pressure of global organ shortages. Organ donation, albeit praised as the “gift of life”, still faces technological or social challenges in the process of procurement and allocation, which might be even daunting when it comes to “gifts” that are in a sub-healthy state because of the donor’s age, disease, trauma, etc. Through an ethnographic study of S Hospital in Guangzhou, China, this article focuses on the interactions between actors involved in the activities, from the procurement of marginal kidneys to their transplantation, and illustrates how the concept and value of marginal donors are (re)constructed in organ-transplantation practice grounded on the theory of biocapital. The article argues that the distribution of organs also means that of risks, and recipients invest their futures through the purchase of transplant services. Under the control of the computer system, organs, as the “gifts of life”, drift downstream along the waiting list, and simultaneously are screened and interpreted by hospitals and are selected and consumed by recipients, while marginal organs, given their potential risks, considerably prolong the drifting journey and increase the uncertainty of transplantation and follow-up care. As the combination of technology and capital continuously shapes modern bio-medicinal regimes, we prospect this research open up a new space to further explore the capitalization characteristics and risk-sharing mechanisms of marginal donors.

Obligation and “Gift of Life”: Code Status Discussions Amongst Potential Recipients in the Transplant Setting *Suze Berkhout, University of Toronto; Kelly Fritsch, Carleton University; Kathleen Sheehan, Centre for Mental Health-University Health Network*

The challenge of communicating the decision to withhold or provide cardiopulmonary resuscitation in seriously ill, hospitalized patients demands the attention of a wide range of health care professionals. In many areas of medicine, discussions about the goals of care must take an array of factors into consideration: how an initial code status question ought to be framed; who should be involved in these discussions and when; and even what the very meaning of “do not resuscitate” itself ought to be. Code status and goals of care discussions take on new meaning within the setting of solid organ transplant. The scarcity of organs available for transplantation has meant that principles of justice and medical utility must be balanced—including clinical considerations of who is reasonably able to survive organ waitlisting as well as transplantation surgery itself, in addition to psychosocial considerations of how potential recipients will cope with the challenges pre- and post-transplantation. Part of these considerations are whether a person unequivocally wants transplantation. This concern intersects with the issue of goals of care as an individual’s desire and commitment to transplantation is tacitly operationalized through their code status. But should this be the case? Taking up a case study of end stage liver disease, we consider the question of code status in light of meeting the challenges of balancing justice, respect for persons, equity, and medical utility, and unpack the social norms and values that currently operate in the transplant setting.

The Politics of Putting Pig Parts into People: The Science and Imaginaries of Xenotransplantation *Joshua Earle, Virginia Tech*

When Martine Rothblatt’s daughter developed a rare lung condition -- often fatal and too uncommon for “big pharma” to produce profitable treatments -- she founded her own biotech company in order to find a cure. United Therapeutics, within 5 years, produced a treatment which saved her daughter’s life, and many others to date. Rothblatt was not satisfied with the treatment, however, because it only delayed the inevitable lung transplant that those with this disease would eventually need, and there are orders of magnitude more people waiting for a transplant than available organs. In order to overcome this gap in organ availability she acquired Revivicor -- a biotech company spun off from the lab that produced Dolly the Sheep -- in order to genetically alter pigs to produce organs transplantable into human subjects. Rothblatt is also a central (and controversial) figure in the Transhumanism movement. Transhumanists seek to use science and technology to improve the human condition, including things like increasing intelligence and physical capabilities, curing disease, and making humans effectively immortal. In this talk, I will discuss both the science of xenotransplantation as Revivicor and United Therapeutics practice it, as well as many of the ethical concerns, particularly as they relate to the stated goals and ethics of the transhumanist movement, and those from Disability Studies that transhumanists usually ignore. I argue that this project cannot be considered ethical under the sentientist framework within which Transhumanism operates, and discuss explicit and possible justifications for the project.

Session Organizer:

Kelly Fritsch, Carleton University

Chair:

Suze Berkhout, University of Toronto

195. Cultivating Justice-Oriented Science: Insights from Collaborative Research Initiatives

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Participants:

A Critical Feminist Rolls Into A Toxicology Lab... *Melina Packer, University of California, Riverside*

Drawing from my ethnographic research in US-based toxicology labs, in this paper I share environmental toxicologists' anonymized responses to learning about their discipline's ongoing colonial legacies, as revealed by my doctoral research and that of other historians of science (Nash 2008; Packer 2020). I also reflect on my own methodological and ethical process in deciding how to present my critical feminist analyses of their discipline. I then share some fruits of our care-full, collaborative labors (Beckett and Keeling 2019), including, for example, co-created reading lists and regularly scheduled lab meetings on critical feminist science studies. I close with visions for deeper, more transformative engagements across and betwixt social and natural scientists, as well as arts and humanities scholars and practitioners (McKittrick 2021). How might we move beyond a simply additive process of interdisciplinarity? In what ways can critical feminist science studies change how (toxicological/scientific) knowledge is produced, and for whose benefit, with explicit commitments to racial, reproductive, and environmental justice? Beckett, Caitlynn, and Arn Keeling. 2019. "Rethinking Remediation: Mine Reclamation, Environmental Justice, and Relations of Care." *Local Environment* 24(3):216–30. McKittrick, Katherine. 2021. *Dear Science and Other Stories*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press. Nash, Linda. 2008. "Purity and Danger: Historical Reflections on the Regulation of Environmental Pollutants." *Environmental History* 13(4):651–58. Packer, Melina. 2020. "Finding the Man in the Glyphosate." PhD Dissertation, University of California, Berkeley, Berkeley, CA.

Biosocial beginnings: building interdisciplinary collaboration in a preconception trial *Michelle Pentecost, Kings College London*

Life course scientists are turning to the preconception period as a window of opportunity to shape intergenerational health. Clinical trials that intervene in the preconception period and measure outcomes in the next generation offer novel methods of testing these hypotheses. These new scientific approaches raise important questions: what does it mean to intervene 'preconception'? The 'preconception' focus could productively emphasise the wide range of social determinants of health, but also has the potential for a loss of gains in reproductive rights and gender equality, and diminished attention to the social drivers of health inequities. In this talk I introduce the Trajectories project. Trajectories partners with the South African arm of a novel multi-country preconception trial - the Healthy Life Trajectories Initiative - to investigate the social and ethical implications of public health interventions in the early life period, and to develop innovative qualitative methodologies for studying the social factors that shape life trajectories. Drawing on feminist STS scholarship, I consider the preconception trial as a novel site of epidemiological knowledge production I and explore the challenges and opportunities such an experiment offers for interdisciplinary, participant-led and justice-oriented research.

Caring for (In)equalities in Multispecies Knowledge Production – Tinkering with the Method of Place-Making *Emilie Moberg, Stockholm University*

The Anthropocene is a proposed geological term describing an epoch which is marked by the significant changes humans have made to the earth's geology and eco systems. However, feminist technoscience scholars, among others, have been reluctant of using the term due to the human-centric, technocentric and Western-centric imaginaries it brings with it. In particular, the human as a 'single geological force' needs to be de-stabilized in order for multiple human bodies and affects to be included as stake-holders in controversies around human-generated climatic, biological and geological transformations. In the present study I will zoom in on one field of knowledge production within the natural sciences, which becomes central to the controversies on climate change; biodiversity. The current study aims to tinker with the method of place-making, drawing on the field of citizen

science, in order to adapt the method to an early childhood education setting. The method will be carried out as a collaboration with a preschool and will consist of picking out and staging a local site, an outdoor place, where knowledge production processes on biodiversity could take place. In this site preschool children aged 4-5, teachers and different kinds of tools and technologies, along with the researchers, will explore and document the variety of species. Apart from staging a site, the current study also aims to study these knowledge production processes in terms of the intimate relations arising between technology, humans and other species in that site. Two questions are asked: What kind of relationships and kinships are formed in the specific place and what kind of knowledge on biological diversity arise from encounters in the place? In what ways do these relationships and kinships produce Environmental (in)equalities in terms of multiple knowledge productions on biodiversity?

Climate Change: Possibility, Critique and the Bleeding Edge Already at Work in the World *Adam Fleischmann, McGill University*

In this paper, I address the paradox of the relation between possibilities and power in the Anthropocene and its attendant crises—specifically, global anthropogenic climate change. As a problem domain originating in science, climate change poses theoretical questions and productive problems. With its complex system dynamics and mind-bending scales, it is changing the possibility of doing politics (Knox 2020). In addressing the exceptional challenges posed by global climate change, scholars in STS and related fields look to critique the institutions, theories and visions of the world that led us to this moment. Yet in practicing critique, how can we engage in the creation and communication of new forms of politics—the art of living together, and, hence, ethics and relations—without deepening exploitative power relations? How do we attend—conceptually, politically—to the contingencies of certain theories or political commitments, while nonetheless actively supporting the people whose life-worlds are threatened by a changing climate, other injustices, exploitation or oppression? Drawing out the generative tension between inherited conceptual frameworks and the empirical problems at hand, I focus on the concept of possibility as it plays out in my ethnographic research on climate change NGOs. Here I focus on one particular group. They use interactive simple climate-policy models, combined with their experience-based learning games and workshops, to create experiences for people to learn for themselves about the system dynamics of climate science and policy, and in doing so, attend to a bleeding edge of possibility already at work in the world.

Pedagogies for Justice-Oriented Change in STEM Research *Sarah Reboloso McCullough, Feminist Research Institute, UC Davis; Kalindi Vora, University of California Davis*

Many researchers enter STEM fields hoping to enact positive change, but the demands of the curriculum and norms of the field leave little room for inquiry and training into the sociocultural implications of the research. These researchers seek other outlets for their activist desires or may end up leaving science. This is particularly true for those historically excluded from STEM. The Asking Different Questions program, whose name tributes the work of Deboleena Roy (2008), provides STS/ethnic studies training for STEM researchers. The program has been a success, with hundreds of participants in the first three-month series and encouraging reviews. A triad of three key elements account for this success: (1) content driven by feminist STS and ethnic studies, (2) a format informed by feminist pedagogy, and (3) an ethos of collectivity. Feminist STS and ethnic studies provided a research-based framework exposing incongruities and challenges of science. Feminist pedagogy allowed participants to bring in their expertise based in lived experience and engage in critical discussion. An ethos of collectivity drew upon tools from community organizing and movement work to give participants

strategies to address large, systemic challenges. As a whole, this allowed participants to leave the training valuing the insights of STS and ethnic studies and actively seeking ways to apply the lessons. 89% of attendees planned to take action based on what they learned in the training. Actions ranged from incorporating indigenous science into the microbiology classroom to diversifying data sets in studying disease prevention to fostering less hierarchical lab cultures.

The Science We Are For: Practicing Collaboration, Justice, and Collectivity *Salvador Zarate, University of California, Irvine; Leslie Quintanilla; Christoph Hanssmann, San Francisco State University; Kalindi Vora, University of California Davis; Lilly Irani, University of California, San Diego; Saiba Varma, University of California San Diego*
“To what extent do we expect science and politics to be separate? To what extent should science, technology and medicine be interested in questions of justice?” So begins the STAR Feminist Co*Lab guidebook entitled *The Science We Are For*. The guidebook’s authors came together in 2018 as part of a research residency to explore methods of collaboration in feminist STS. Working with and against the critical currents of STS, this “pocket guide” offers a tool for teaching and practicing science for and with our communities. The project responds to repeated failures on the part of STEM practitioners to ask questions and design methods that have direct and immediate benefits for communities most affected by technoscientific interventions. Instead, it asks: Who is science for? How do we bring science in the service of people not profit? And what truth making practices are up to the task of liberation? Scientific critique is one means through which to address these questions. However, its transformative potential will be limited without methods to build connections, relations, collaborations, and infrastructures of exchange. This guidebook synthesizes feminist science studies with critical race and ethnic studies, studies of reproductive labor, transnational organizing, and transformative community-based politics to attend to the stakes of justice-oriented science, technology, and medicine. The presentation will discuss: 1) the “slow collaborative research” involved in writing the guidebook; 2) its format and desired audiences; 3) its cross-disciplinary applications in teaching and research; and 4) its overall contribution to STS in research, pedagogy, and field-building.

Session Organizer:

Martha Kenney, San Francisco State University

196. Regulating Medical Devices (or Not): Standards, Evidence, and the Political Economy of Medical Device Innovation - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Despite the proliferation of STS scholarship on biomedicalization, pharmaceuticalization, and geneticization, studies interrogating the social construction, regulation, and political economy of medical devices remain slim. Yet, past studies have shown how medical devices and technologies are rich sites for STS investigation. Medical devices are increasingly used in routine clinical care, and include a broad range of objects from MRI machines to assays to surgical implants. Medical devices are regulated in a variety of ways depending on national contexts. In the United States, medical devices, unlike pharmaceuticals, often come to market without rigorous safety and efficacy testing or clinical trials. This regulatory environment purports to encourage innovation, but it also creates uncertainty surrounding potential harm to the public. What regulatory regimes exist in different nations to approve and govern medical devices and innovation? What standards of proof are needed to gain regulatory approval in particular contexts? How do the ways in which medical devices are regulated impact patient care and safety? How does medical device innovation shape scientific knowledge about human bodies, health, and illness? What shapes the political economies of medical device development, adoption, and use? We seek empirical contributions that explore questions about the political economy and regulation of medical

technologies and devices, their construction, and the developers who create them. We particularly are interested in papers that examine the implications of emergent medical technologies and devices for inequality and health justice.

Participants:

Got the point; lost the point: Innovating Acupuncture through Standards and Regulations *Wen-Hua Kuo, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University*

The paper looks at institutional attempts to make acupuncture a standardized medical device for study and for practice. A peculiar way of treating people via meridians inside their bodies punctuated by regulatory points, acupuncture has been used as a therapy for thousands of years, without losing popularity after the wide acceptance of bio-medicine in East Asia. Furthermore, its popularity increases outside of East Asia. Focusing on the endeavor to lay a scientific foundation for acupuncture, this project traces proposals brought by the World Health Organization, the International Standard Organization, and organizations dominated by East Asian states and analyzes what they have achieved in terms of standardization. Departing from a simple interpretation that claims such negotiations as purely diplomatic in the political context of East Asia, this project aims to explore the changing meaning of acupuncture as it is disputed among the experts assigned to establish standards. In particular, it investigates three kinds of technical guidance concerning the practice of acupuncture: a product standard for acupuncture needles, the nomenclature of acupuncture points and their locations, and the guideline on the procedure of acupuncture. It argues that these attempts for acupuncture not only have given this art a semiotic/marital identity, in which the body of practitioner and the patient’s body are universal and thus their interactions can be regulated. They also established a tangible framework by which acupuncture transforms and evolves in the twenty-first century. Like Pablo Picasso claims in the case of painting, “Learn the rules like a pro, so you can break them like an artist.”

Operations for Excess: Situating Surgical Interventions for Palmar Hyperhidrosis in Taiwan *Jia-shin Chen, Institute of Science, Technology and Society, National Yang Ming Chiao Tung University (NYCU)*

People sweat, but some people sweat excessively in areas such as palms. A medical diagnosis, palmar hyperhidrosis, describes this condition. The prevalence of palmar hyperhidrosis is allegedly high in Taiwan, so many treatments are applied. Among them, surgical intervention, which aims to interrupt the thoracic sympathetic fibers innervating sweat glands of the palm, is the most noted. Techniques for treating palmar hyperhidrosis underwent several major changes in the past few decades. A specific type of operative method, video-assisted endoscopic thoracic sympathectomy (ETS), eventually prevailed as the most adopted approach in Taiwan. This easy-to-learn technique was made possible by assembling several surgical tools into a technological system, and it became popular among both surgeons and patients. However, side effects gradually surfaced years later, and a small fraction of operated patients resented having received this treatment. Their complaints resulted in bureaucratic intervention, which mandated that such operations could only be allowed with a permission granted by the Ministry of Health. Afterward, ETS operations shrunk vastly in number, and people with palmar hyperhidrosis now turn to less invasive methods. The presentation intends to conceptualize the development and regulation of these techniques, now rarely applied, as situated among multidirectional vectors that took hold in a specific time in Taiwan.

"Price doesn't matter"?: The prescription of anti-cancer drugs in two French public hospitals *Pierre-André Juven, CNRS*

The arrival on the market of many products including immunotherapies, gene therapies or more broadly what has been

called targeted therapies, is nowadays a concern for NGOs, governments and even institutions such as the OECD. All these actors have constituted the prize for innovations against cancer as a public problem. This construction of a public problem implies of course antagonisms, different interpretations of the problem and the solutions that need to be found. Many sociological studies and researches in political science have worked for several years on the controversies related to the regulation of the price of innovations. These works show especially how competing concerns about the pharmaceutical industry (access to care, employment, encouraging innovation, budgetary rigour) are confronted. To observe these “luxury products”, cancer treatments, it is also possible to get as close as possible to their use and observe what their price does to those who handle them, buy them and prescribe them. Few surveys have examined the reality of this problem in clinical services and the effects of these prices on carers and administrative actors. This is what we propose to present in this paper based on two ethnographic surveys of five weeks each in two French hospitals, and a series of semi-directive interviews. We show that the noise that this problem tends to create outside the hospital is strangely absent in almost all exchanges and places within the institution. This invisibility that we are exposing nevertheless requires a detailed analysis, because although the price is rarely actual in these areas, its virtual presence provides information on the medical and economic challenges it poses to cancer care.

The role of freezing devices in the Spanish IVF economy: practices of coupling and decoupling eggs and embryos *Sara Lafuente-Funes, Institute for Sociology, Goethe University, Frankfurt*

Cryopreservation is a key technology within human assisted reproduction. Even though embryos and sperm have been routinely frozen since the 1980s, cryopreservation of eggs remained difficult until the emergence of vitrification. The last decade has witnessed a rapid expansion in the use of this technique, particularly in Spain, making it possible to freeze eggs to preserve fertility and to store them in banks. Also, this technique has increased success rates for embryo thawing, opening the door to a new range of practices including an expansion of embryo testing. A close look at how vitrification works in the Spanish context shows that the use of a particular device, cryotop®, is key to its functioning. This device, a platform in which eggs or embryos are placed in order to be immersed in liquid nitrogen, is entangled in ways of grouping eggs and embryos that have further consequences for the ways in which they are used. These groupings are of central importance in the functioning of the growing egg bank industry, which specialises in distributing batches of eggs for clinics within and across borders. This paper analyses the role that these devices play in a complex network of changes and continuities within assisted reproduction made possible by vitrification. We engage with practices of decoupling and grouping eggs and embryos in the process of freezing and thawing using this device, and pose questions about the consequences of these strategies for embryo selection and rejection, and for egg providers, recipients and reproductive markets.

Session Organizers:

Melanie Jeske, University of California, San Francisco
Kelly Joyce, Drexel University

197. Diseased Landscapes: Health and Illness in Territories of Extraction - II - DISCLOSURE AND CONCEALMENT

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Through the theme of Diseased Landscapes, this panel explores how the nexus of extractivism and political conflict affects environmental and human health. It aims at bringing together efforts in scholarly practice—including art-based methodologies and activist-oriented research—to historically, politically, and socially situate disease, toxins, pathogens, non-

humans, and bodily dysfunction in violent geographies produced by legal and illegal extractivism. We ask how the health conditions of the environment and the body become entangled in places dominated by extractivist economies. What difference does it make to tell stories of armed violence, gendered and racialized dispossession, capitalism, mining, and agrarian expansion through human and more-than-human experiences of health and illness? How are evidence and ignorance about bodies and landscapes produced, used, and abused in contexts marked by extractivist activities? And finally, what practices, methods, and interventions are helpful to establish good relations, capable of disrupting the combined production of disease and violence in old, new, and future territories of extraction?

Participants:

Indeterminate contamination: arsenic and gold extraction in Brazil *Isabela Noronha*

The city of Paracatu has the largest Brazilian open pit for gold extraction; at the same time, gold itself is found in the lowest concentration in the world. For mining to be profitable, it needs a monumental effort of exposing and dismantling the rocks. Besides the monstrous tailings dams, it can also create a less visible residue: arsenic. The aim of this work is to discuss controversies surrounding this particular kind of residue that is left behind after mining. Gold deposits in Paracatu are found associated with arsenopyrite, which when exposed can release some substances, like arsenic, in a chemical reaction called acid mining drainage. Once disturbed, these substances then create other forms of relation, inhabiting soils, water and bodies. There is no safe limit for arsenic in human bodies and it can take years until they show some evidence. In Paracatu, several inhabitants have developed chronic diseases that could be related to arsenic contamination, and they demand responsabilization of the mining company; the company, in return, argues that arsenic could be found naturally all over the region due to rock composition, so the mine cannot be accounted. I argue that what is at stake is more than the ambiguous natural/technological source of contamination, but the complete indeterminacy surrounding every step of this conflict. The slippery character of these residues to escape regulatory mechanisms; the foggy paths among regulation, assessments and reports, as well as politics of knowledge production all contribute to create an entangled environment of slow violences.

Living with Disease: Concealing Illness on the Congolese Copperbelt, 1970s-2010s *Iva Pesa, University of Groningen*

Large-scale resource extraction, of copper, cobalt, zinc and uranium, has caused devastating environmental change on the Congolese Copperbelt. Protracted mining throughout the twentieth century left inevitable marks on workers' bodies and the health of urban residents. A unique archival collection of medical records in the town of Likasi, from the 1970s onwards, allows me to trace different perceptions of health and disease and how this was influenced by the mining industry. Doctors, mine engineers and workers had different understandings of what constituted safe working conditions or emission levels. Knowledge about health and disease was moreover contested and sometimes concealed. Doctors argued that silicosis was caused by smoking or old age, rather than mining employment. By relying on oral history, I will ask why workers long accepted the health risks posed by mining. Their relationship with the mines as paternalistic employers and the repressive one-party regime provided the context in which Likasi's residents learnt to live with disease. After 2000, this regime of disease imperceptibility started to dissolve, as privatised mining companies instituted neoliberal policies and workers became more vocal in demanding their rights to a healthy environment.

Pathogenic Politics: Industrial Salmon and the Making of a Viral Ecology in the Salish Sea *Darcey Evans, University Of California At Santa Cruz*

In the coastal waters of British Columbia (BC), Canada, Piscine

orthoreovirus (PRV) a virus that spreads rapidly among fish in open-net aquaculture farms of Atlantic salmon- has stoked anxieties around the ambiguous circulation of and potential danger posed by viral shedding. PRV travels through supply chains, ocean currents, and ecological interactions, and causes salmon to become at risk of ruptured blood cells and organ damage. Concerns over inter-species transfer of the virus are especially pronounced since Atlantic salmon farms in BC are located on critical Pacific salmon migration routes. In this paper, I propose that PRV can be understood as a form of industrial waste that illuminates historical, social, and ecological processes within the bodies and blood cells of fish. I first outline how the inability to confirm PRV's origins and disease-causing capabilities contributes to instability within and beyond the institutions charged with managing fish health. I then describe how multiple forms of life, ecological encounters, and unique hydrological conditions become entangled with industrial practices, giving rise to novel pathogenic proliferations. I end by discussing how the bodily forms of fish can tell stories of ecological encounter and colonial entanglement in ways that enable settler-colonial occupation to be made visible within the waterscape. This paper contributes to STS by forging connections between settler-colonialism, industrial landscape-making, and pathogenicity, in order to highlight how microbes can reflect and reinforce settler-colonial structures of dispossession in that ways that continue to unfold beyond the boundaries of industrial projects.

Sick Plants, Sick People: the Public Health of Monocrops
Kregg Hetherington, Concordia University

Ever since the Atlantic forest of eastern Paraguay began to be replaced by soybeans, the ideal monocropped landscape has been afflicted with constant agrarian ailments: erosion, milkweed, leaf beetles, rust. Each of these has been met by agronomists as a technical challenge, and a vast phytosanitary apparatus has been built up around it including not only new techniques and chemical cures, but governmental techniques for biological control. But as in other, better-known agrarian contexts, the medicine applied to diseased landscapes soon begat diseases of other kinds: respiratory and skin conditions among farmers, and the slow clustering of cancers. Moreover, soybeans became a classic case of what Rob Nixon called "slow violence," gradually producing not only disease but, economic inequality, an erosion of welfare provisions, ethnic tensions and captive bureaucracies, and contributing inexorably to a warming planet. Based in an ethnographic study of the Paraguayan case, this paper explores the historical relationships between phytosanitary and public health regimes, the many institutions that accrue around industrial agriculture and the different sorts of populations that thrive and die with them. Suggesting an analytics for this agribiopolitical assemblage, the paper shows how languages of more-than-human health familiar to farmers, agronomists and phytosanitary policy-makers, speak to the diseased material entanglements with which our siloed approaches to human and non-human health often have trouble grappling.

Wet Air: Living within an Atmosphere of Extraction
Zsuzsanna Dominika Ihar, University of Sydney

To breathe in the air of NZS—a semi-makeshift settlement hugging the AzərNəftYağ refinery—, is akin to drinking a glass of water. Due to the emission of high quantities of methane, the flaring of waste, asphalt blowing, and the general heat produced by the processing units, an atmosphere of wetness and moisture pervades the entire neighbourhood. Residents regularly complain of blurred vision, oily residue on skin, mouldy black walls, and the inability to properly dry clothes, as gaseous compounds turn liquid. In this paper, I draw upon Mel Y. Chen's 'toxic sensoriums' in order to trace the movement and conversion of hydrocarbon molecules—from flare stack to skin. I argue that the body becomes forcefully incorporated into the extractive apparatus through the creation of unescapable atmospheres,

which infiltrate every pore, every room, and every cell. However, for marginal communities, it also becomes a mode of sensing and evidencing harm, providing tactile proof of physical injury and ecological contamination. Indeed, the presence of wet (or oily) air has generated an array of everyday strategies of mediation, allowing the settlement to remain despite acute toxicity, irritation, and increasing pressure by authorities to relocate to the outskirts of the city. In the concluding section of the paper, I introduce examples of speculative methods which were workshopped with members of the local community—including amateur purification instruments and the creation of experimental 'dry mints'.

Session Organizer:

Javier Lezaun, University of Oxford

Chair:

Lina Beatriz Pinto-García, Universidad de los Andes

Discussant:

Diana Ojeda, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

198. Disempowerment and Empowerment with Autonomous and Intelligent Systems II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

The relationship between artificial intelligence technology and power is widely discussed, both in the STS community and more broadly. While ethical decision making in the development of AI has been the subject of literally hundreds of frameworks in the past half decade, the consideration of power and AI has been almost entirely absent. The 420,000-member technology professional organization IEEE, through its Standards Association (author of the Ethically Aligned Design report) and its Society on Social Implications of Technology, is developing a discussion of how to prioritize the distribution rather than concentration of power in the development of AI technology. Insights from STS play an important part in examining power and technology. A report in preparation focusses on three aspects, past, present, and future. Past is historical, rediscovering technology's diverse origins, and considering the decolonial. Present draws on legal expertise, the way in which technology currently enforces power. Future is creative, what we could do better. The presentations in this panel each contribute an insight to the issue of power and technology.

Participants:

Algorithmic Content Moderation and the Conspiratorial Common Sense of Facebook Groups
Lee Gensler, CUNY Graduate Center

How can algorithms that govern social media platforms be designed in ethical and transparent ways that both foster community growth and effectively target dangerous groups? And how has the current opaque configuration of automated content moderation on Facebook fueled conspiratorial thinking and misidentified hate and misinformation? Over 1.8 billion people are members of Facebook groups, a fast-growing portion of Facebook's platform. In many ways, groups are a contemporary version of what internet forums once offered—a place to connect with strangers over shared experiences and interests. But while all of the labor of creating and sustaining groups is done by unpaid users, Facebook ultimately has complete control over these spaces, and every group exists in constant fear of being disappeared. Groups develop extensive rules meant to prevent getting zucked, the popular term for being deleted by Facebook. A reference to Mark Zuckerberg, the term points to the complete control over the platform attributed to higher-ups at Facebook. But of course, Mark Zuckerberg isn't combing through group posts. Instead, an opaque algorithm automates the process of identifying content that violates Facebook's community standards and determining which groups are disabled. To explore these questions about the sociality of Facebook groups and platform governance, I draw on a year of digital ethnography conducted in a group dedicated to COVID-19 education, where I have taken on the role of moderator, observed the group as it

grew to over 26,000 members, and navigated the response to the group being erroneously disabled by Facebook

A New Power-Triangle Within the Organization: Structural Power Differentials Between Workers, Managers, and AI Systems *Andreas Deppeler; Devesh Narayanan, Centre on AI Technology for Humankind, National University of Singapore*

STS scholarship has seen recent interest in analysing “structural” differentials of power and resources. One relatively underexplored space for such analysis, we suggest, is within contemporary organizations. This is particularly so because, as AI systems are increasingly being deployed to assist in a variety of organizational functions, existing power differentials between workers and managers are being amplified and altered in new ways. In this paper, we develop an account of a “power triangle” in the contemporary organization – where, through their interactions, workers, managers, and AI systems each dominate and are dominated by each other in distinct ways. This account draws mainly from three scholarly traditions. We draw from research in information systems and operations management to categorize the types of interactions between workers, managers, and technology. We then draw from STS to characterize these human-technology interactions as exercises of power. In particular, we are influenced by theories of technological mediation and various existing accounts of the use of technology to exert socio-political power. Finally, we draw from research in critical management studies in general, and labour process theory in particular, to situate these exercises of power within broader structures of domination and subordination in organizations. Along the way, we illustrate the explanatory potential of our account with examples of current use-cases of AI in organizations. In so doing, we find new ways to describe how workers are currently dominated at work, while also sketching new pathways for worker emancipation.

Extending Power Asymmetries with Persona Constructs: critiquing strategies of humanitarian design *Natalie Florence Severy, Arizona State University*

The emergency shelter is an architectural response to humanitarian crises. The metrics of success and failure of emergency shelters have focused on the potential of emergency shelters to improve quality of life for refugees. A successful product promises to liberate people and decrease human suffering. However, to date there is limited critique of how designers identify the specific needs of refugees living in encampment. Power asymmetries prevent refugees from being treated as equal and valued stakeholders, limiting the potential for democratic, co-production strategies. In this study the Better Shelter is addressed as a case study which exemplifies these imbalances of power. Better Shelter is a transitional housing unit designed for deployment for refugee camps worldwide. Rather than including refugees in co-creation, the product designers engaged in constructing personas, a tool used by designers to create fictionalized settings and solicit empathy. However, assumptions made with persona constructs often reflect values of the designers more than they do the clients themselves (Long, 2009). A Grounded Theory approach is used to extract the probable constituents for persona constructions of the Better Shelter and the UNHCR. These constructs target high-risk groups of people under forced duress. This paper argues how the discourse in the marking of the Better Shelter is consistent with historical strategies of humanitarian aid, which constructed narratives of the suffering of others to solicit empathy. The intention of the paper is to advance the understanding of how constructing personas is a design tool that undermines co-creation and extends power symmetries. Within STS scholarship there is much needed research on interrogating power asymmetries in assemblages of sociotechnical artifacts.

Session Organizer:

Greg Adamson, IEEE SSIT

199. Nonhuman Phenomenology and Technoscientific Intersubjectivity - 1: Designing Intersubjectivity

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Participants:

Cultivating Artificial Flowers *Antonia von Schoening, University Of Basel, Switzerland*

The paper first looks at the curious tradition of arranging flowers made of paper, silk, or plastic and contemplating their immutable visual appearance. While these artificial flowers take on a purely decorative function, two contemporary art projects explore the entanglement of technical, human, plant, and animal agencies to reflect on care and response-ability in interspecies-relationships: In Anna Ridler's "Mosaic Virus" (2019) an AI generates short moving images of tulips, referencing the complex history of horticulture, migration, and capitalist greed for profit as well as still life painting in 17th-century Holland. For "Non Flowers for a Hoverfly" (2020) Thomas Pausz uses new technologies to design virtual boundary objects that interact with insects in order to better understand and encourage the pollination of other, presumably natural, flowers. Both projects underline the importance of translating between the material and tangible and the virtual and imaginary dimensions of cultivating (artificial) flowers. Both aim at technically creating interspecies environments in order to learn about human and non-human perception and behavior and to create empathy with non-human entities.

Doing Partial Affinity with Plants *Danial Qaurooni, 325 E. 10th St.*

Nagel's philosophical lament (1974) that he will never know what it is like to be a bat assumes what Despret (2013) has called empathy by identification. Here, empathy can flow across given, if not a priori, similarities between two terms, which in Nagel's example are two natural kinds: human and bat. Other approaches to nonhuman relations (e.g. analytic, phenomenological, or bio-semiotic) often share Nagel's assumption that identity is a prerequisite for empathy and as such should precede it. Reversing this order, Despret (2013) introduces relations that are forged out of identities that are constructed rather than inherited and partial (Strathern 1988) rather than whole. This reversal opens up the process of identification, allowing unexpected affinities between the two terms that had been foreclosed by Nagel's essentialism. Disclosing such unexpected affinities is one way of building creative relations with plants. In this presentation, I explore three examples of partial affinities with plants in, a prose-poem by Francis Ponge, a sculpture by Paul Morrison, and a speculative design by the author. Each of these encounters is a partial affinity, a mutual opening, between plants on the one hand and words, people, and technologies on the other. Woefully incomplete and mostly un-romantic, such affinities nevertheless offer Nagel some hope, if he is willing to meet the universe halfway (Barad 2007).

Extending sensibility for metabolic processes in immersive media environments *Desiree Förster, University of Chicago*

How can we experience the relation to our surroundings as processual and at the same time meaningful? Not from a perspective that is solely functional oriented but as the expression of meaning that lies in the nature of our relational being itself? In this paper I explore how a new aesthetics of atmospheres in spatial installations can heighten our sensitivity for ecological interdependencies (external) and at the same time for the responsiveness of our bodies previous to semantic reference (internal). In this responsiveness I locate an openness towards patterns in the internal and external surroundings that allow a specific situation to make sense for a perceiving subject. I aim to flesh out how aesthetic practices explore different ways of

engaging with the materiality of atmospheres and how they relate to our imaginative capacity. I will present art installations that bring together several human and nonhuman agents: air, water, clouds, and micro-organisms like algae. Different aesthetic registers enable in these environments ways to be-out-of-oneself. One of the presented works is a VR environment I co-developed with artists, which represents a natural surrounding in which the participants' respiration impacts the growth of virtual plants. The participants experience the correlation of their own metabolic processes, the photosynthesis of the plants, and the rising temperature in the surrounding with different sense modalities.

Follow Pull Avoid Sync Limit: Music-Making With Virtual Bird Flocks *Einar Engström, Science and Technology Studies, York University*

This paper concerns the contemporary computer music practice of composing with and alongside simulations of artificial life. Departing from histories of the animated representation of life on-screen (cf. Kelty and Landecker 2004), programmer-musicians have increasingly translated such theories to the audible (cf. Miranda et al. 2003). Genetic algorithms, cellular automata, L-systems, and other behavioral models abandon their formal roles in biology, mathematics, and computer science to morph into structural paradigms for mediation by musical assemblage (Born 2005). As knowledge about nonhuman life and its attendant worlds thus locks into the sonic, the affective, and the precognitive, I explore where meaning itself lands. What can be known from "growing" music? What and where is the sense in writing a computer music script based on emergent behavior? How can one think with relational world-making in virtual music-making with Others? Taking an ethnographic approach, I follow boids.lua, a computer music variation on the "Boids" bird flocking algorithm developed in mid-1980s computer graphics research, as it emerges in the monome/Whimsical Raps "ecosystem" of open-source, intelligent musical instruments. Hovering in the in-between of sound, computing, and human and nonhuman sensibility, I parse code, community, composition, and listening through one another so as to construct a "tehoustemology" (Greene and Porcello 2005) of a "sonic way in knowing and being in the world." This turns to a questioning of a hearing "in excess of the ear" (Scrimshaw 2013): of sonic affect embedded in navigational systems of birds.

Session Organizer:

Claire Isabel Webb, University of Southern California

Chair:

Richard Fadok, MIT

200. Dissolving Boundaries: Creative Practice Meets STS – I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

This set of experimental sessions brings together poets, artists, and musicians alongside STS scholarship and STS approaches in order to explore the role of the nonlinear, the nonverbal, the intuitive, and the gestural in deepening our understanding of climate change, the covid pandemic, and mass extinction -- as well as the scientific response to each of these. The sessions also explore art-science collaborations as a way to generate insight into scientific practice and knowledge, and as a pedagogical method. In addition, some sessions explore not-necessarily-academic knowledge and insight developed via creative interaction with other-than-human beings, as well as through intra- and cross-disciplinary blendings of science, STS, and the arts. Presentations will include readings and performances as well as more traditional inquiry. Session I of this panel focuses on poetry.

Participants:

The overlap between science and poetry: Practice and Teaching
Charles Malone, Wick Poetry Center

This is not a traditional paper, but in addition to my own collection of poems, titled "Working Hypothesis" which is interested in overlap between science and poetry, I will discuss

the #PoetsforScience project (<https://poetsforscience.org/>) the Earth Stanzas/Vote for the Earth projects with the Center for Earth Ethics (<https://vote.earthstanzas.com/>), and my work currently conducting a "Poetic Inventory of Cuyahoga Valley National Park"

(<https://sites.google.com/kent.edu/poeticinventorycvnp/>). I will also discuss developing digital poetry lessons for the Environmental Education Center at CVNP (<https://cvnp.travelingstanzas.com/>).

Research in Bloom: Reflections and explorations of science, art, and writing with the land *Erin Schneider*

Arts-based research practices, such as poetry, support our cultivation and understanding of place and our abilities to evaluate and reflect on lessons learned from different scientific domains—bringing new perspectives to problems and possibilities at hand and dissolve the boundaries that keep art, heart, and science separate. I look forward to highlighting three case studies I've been a part of in my work as a Farmer, Writer, and Educator that demonstrate different ways in which art, poetry in particular, can further our participation with members of the Earth's ecosystems. These include: 1) Community Public Art Project called Unearthing a Soil Quilt: Collaborations with the Soil as part of the 2015 U.N. International Year of the Soil Celebration; 2) 2019 Development of a Farmer/Writer in Residence Program with Michigan State Universities Kellogg Biological Research Center and how poetry and art were part of engaging researchers, students, and the community in expressing the shared allurements and learning about the science on site; and 3) 2021 Currently a writing with the land and poetry test plot series as part of a partnership with the land, a local land trust, and sharing the poems that emerge. Participants will have a chance to play with poetry and will leave with a prompt or two for considering ways to partner with the humosphere and fellow humans in a way that mutually amplifies the relationships of each. Results of our time together will combine the visual, the verbal, and (potentially) the edible.

Session Organizer:

Christine Wenc, Arts + Literature Laboratory / Greenwood History

201. A Good Life, In Theory: Thinking and Living with Climate Change - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

In recent years, an increasing amount of STS and STS-aligned scholarship has used provocative and conceptually creative ways to address the exceptional challenges posed by global climate change. A number of theoretical orientations have emerged within Anthropocene studies, such as new materialism and Gaia-based approaches, offering sophisticated ways for scholars to think through the implications of climate change for both human and more-than-human life. However, these shifts have also inspired backlash from those who argue that the constant search for new theory obfuscates empirical realities and the politics of responsibility. Particularly in light of the climate crisis, the at-times tenuous and overlapping relationships between theoretical creativity, empirical rigor, and everyday action demand renewed critical attention. This panel seeks to critically engage these fragile relationships within Anthropocene STS scholarship to illuminate potentials for individual, academic, and political meaning in a warming world. How can scholars hold onto both climate realism and creative conceptualizations of more-than-humans? Does the urgency of global warming demand a more overt level of political engagement in academia? Can we effectively reconcile the conceptual utility of our theoretical methodologies with the pragmatic and embodied risks of ecological justice? Papers will address these multiscalar gaps, reframing potential discrepancies as constructive spaces of possibility for good relations between fellow earthlings. Session II, "Affective Futures," gathers papers exploring the affective tensions and contradictions within climate change imaginaries. Themes include the political implications of climate anxiety; the reconciliation of abstract science with personal stakes;

oscillations between life and death, hope and defeatism.

Participants:

“Good Vibes Only” at the End of the World *Cristina Visperas, University of Southern California*

An unprecedented emergency against which leading climate scientists unreservedly propound civilizational change (IPCC, 2018), the problems of global warming and mass extinction not only vex our scientific and humanistic tools for understanding them, but also weigh heavy on our public and personal feelings toward (the value of) human and nonhuman life. How does one stay present with an unthinkable future, whose scale of suffering is described as “incalculable” and “catastrophic” (Scientists’ Statement of Support for Non-Violent Direct Action Against Government Inaction Over the Climate & Ecological Emergency, 2019). To think with climate change is inescapably anxiety-producing. Borrowing from queer and feminist theories on affect, this paper argues for the analytical affordances of emotion - feeling climate change in order to think it (and live it responsibly). The paper analyzes alternative, more accessible ways climate experts have begun to discuss their work, where they replace jargon with intimate stories of how climate change is reshaping their emotional lives in deeply painful ways - how they feel about their relationships, their work, public and policy responses to the looming crisis, and so on. This profoundly sentimental archive constitutes an important foil to cultural and ideological premiums placed on hope and good feeling, which regulate and stunt public attitudes in the face of collective existential calamities that, in fact, might entail the mobilization of negative affect and dark moods rather than their management. With merchants of doubt, we have as well merchants of positive thinking.

Population Anxieties and Uncertain Futures of Nordic

Wellbeing: Exploring the Affective Politics of Demographic Dystopias and Hopes in the Face of Climate Change *Mianna Meskus, Tampere University; Riikka Homanen, University of Tampere*

Decreasing fertility rates and trends toward delaying family formation have been noted across the whole of the Western world, generating deep concern from different stakeholders. Finland is no exception to this. In 2020, the total fertility rate was ‘ultra-low’ at 1.35 children per woman – the lowest it has ever been. Population statistics and demographers single out the year 2010, after which the rate has been on decline. Following this turning point, policymaking and public discussion about the future of the welfare society and its conditions of existence has taken many forms, ranging from population-related anxieties over in/voluntary childlessness, care for the elderly and economic vitality to, albeit cautiously, environmental sustainability. Visions of risky futures and good life have hinged on the affectively charged idea of ‘depopulation’, oscillating between demographic dystopias and hopes. Exploring population anxieties in the age of climate change, our paper analyses the enactment of national futures during intertwined demographic and environmental crises. Drawing from policy and media materials, we focus particularly on contested understandings of reproduction, ageing and migration as biopolitical targets. We aim to show that the challenges of imagining demographically and ecologically viable futures are rooted in and arise from the histories of pronatal population policies, difficult legacies of racial hygienics, and the dominant ideas of ethnic and genetic homogeneity, while the role of the natural environment in the biopolitics of populations remains largely unproblematised.

Practizing Death in the Anthropocene *Hjordis Becker-Lindenthal, The University of Cambridge; Simone Kotva, University of Oslo*

With its emphasis on a post-human planetary future ‘without us’ the concept of the Anthropocene proposes an ethics in which the

afterlife has already begun. In this way the Anthropocene resurrects the ancient ideal of philosophy as a ‘practice for dying and death’ (Plato, Apology 64a3-4). We ask: how do we live responsibly in the present while at the same time paying attention to life after death? and explore one possible answer in the ‘memory and practice of death’ as developed by the ascetical theology of the early Church.

Reckoning Vital Uncertainties: Climate Science, Disaster Ontologies, and Shifting Moral Ecologies in the Nepal Himalayas *Austin Lord, Cornell University*

The Langtang Valley of Nepal is simultaneously a critical site for climate science in the Himalayan region, home for a community struggling to recover from a devastating disaster, and a sacred landscape animated by territorial deities who help make life possible in a precarious world. In 2015, a massive co-seismic glacier avalanche destroyed the ancestral Langtang village, taking life at an unthinkable and unprecedented scale (Lord 2015). As the aftermath unfolded and the Langtangpas worked to rebuild their lives, glaciologists and climatologists also returned to Langtang to continue the work of understanding change processes and forecasting uncertain futures - as climate change is expected to increase avalanche risk across the Himalayas. This paper considers the ways that the 2015 avalanche, understood diachronically, has catalyzed new ethical questions that draw together concerns about epistemological pluralism, climate justice, and situated moral ecologies (cf. Sherpa 2014; Butcher 2017; Gagne 2018). In what ways do multiscale concepts of climate justice articulate with Langtangpa needs to restore relations with local protector deities who can help them cope with the lived uncertainties and future hazards? How might theoretical concerns with political ontology (Blaser 2014; Burman 2017) mix with immediate material needs to respond to the complexity of changing hazard regimes? In what ways have my own entanglements with Langtangpa lives and hopes for the future - as a survivor of the 2015 Langtang event, a post-disaster volunteer, and/or an ethnographer of disaster and climate change (Lord & Murton 2017) - shaped my theoretical and ethical commitments amid these vital uncertainties?

Session Organizer:

Anin Luo, Princeton University

Chair:

Anin Luo, Princeton University

202. Expertise, law, and "reasonable" professional practice

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

This session includes a series of papers on legal efforts to administer and render judgments in specific cases on what counts as reasonable or adequate practice in specific lines of work. Legal investigations and tribunals often involve efforts to examine whether particular actions by members of a profession were consistent with normal practice for that profession. Often experts are called upon to assist investigations and to testify in tribunals about standards and norms that hold for the conduct in question. They are deemed qualified as infra-experts with experience in the relevant specialty and/or as meta-experts who have investigated relevant aspects of the specialty. Cases featured in presentations in this setting include police officers with expertise in "force science" by virtue of personal experience and instruction of others on the topic of use of force, and experts and academics with relevant knowledge of standards of care in medical practice. The session relates to STS research on the uneasy relations between expert and lay knowledge on matters of public concern. It also relates to work on the relations of law and science: both law-in-science, or how legal judgments and standards demarcate "science" from "junk science", and science-in-law, or how scientific authority is enlisted in legal forums.

Participants:

The expert reconstruction of "reasonable" and "unreasonable" use of force in police shootings of suspects *Michael Lynch,*

Cornell Univ.

Expert witnesses on police use of force deploy digital technology to re-visualize video materials to support the prosecution or defense of police officers accused of unjustified and excessive use of force in the apprehension of suspects. In the recent trial of Chicago Police officer Jason Van Dyke, who was charged with the 2014 murder of Laquan McDonald, an expert witness for the defense reconstructed a video of the shooting which had gone viral. The reconstruction animated the scene from Van Dyke's point of view. As in other recent trials, the defense argued that a "reasonable police officer" would view the movements that McDonald was making (or about to make) at the time of the shooting threatened the safety of the officer or other nearby parties. This paper discusses how expert witnesses not only re-interpret video evidence taken at the scene of police uses of force, but also reconstruct the raw video footage into a visual demonstration of "reasonable" actions consistent with training. Such demonstrations do not necessarily convince a jury -- indeed, the jury convicted Van Dyke of murder -- but they provide clear exhibits of how "perspective," "interpretation," and "intention" are turned into visual exhibits designed to support adversary narratives. The paper delves into the practices through which video evidence is reconstructed into exhibits of "reasonable" or "unreasonable" police practice.

Specialists vs Generalists: Finding Common Knowledge Among Reasonable Physicians in Malpractice Trials *Patrick Garon-Sayegh, University of Toronto*

The reasonable physician standard is the cornerstone of medical malpractice law, against which physicians' actions are judged when injured patients accuse them of negligence. But the standard tells lawyers and judges very little on its own; it must be suffused with a case's particulars and the opinion of medical experts called to assess the defendant-physician's actions. To be fair to both parties, the standard must be "calibrated" to the physician's level of specialization. This reflects the medical profession's extensive system of formal credentialing, and the fact that some physicians can be considered "laypersons" when compared to more specialized peers. In legal practice, the need to calibrate entails that expert witnesses are typically called to testify on a "specialist-to-specialist" or "generalist-to-generalist" basis. But since specialists are not completely barred from testifying against generalists (and vice-versa), whether or not the former can testify against the latter ultimately turns on the specifics of each case. This paper examines how lawyers in an Ontario trial argued over whether an infectious diseases specialist ought to be allowed to testify against two emergency physicians accused of having misdiagnosed a fatal infection. Using trial transcripts, the paper shows how the question of whether or not a physician is "properly qualified" to testify against another raises heterogeneous arguments, among which formal credentials play only a small part. It also shows how the categories of "generalist" and "specialist" can be reconfigured to circumscribe common ground between them, according to the local exigencies of a given case.

Posthumous Psychoanalysis: On Assigning 'Motive' to a Victim of Police Violence *Patrick Watson, Wilfrid Laurier University*

The 2016 criminal trial of Toronto Police Service's Constable James Forcillo in the shooting death of Sammy Yatim included a series of noteworthy and novel findings and arguments. Among these was an attempt by Forcillo's counsel to introduce an expert witness, criminologist and ex-police officer Rick Parent, to argue Yatim engaged in victim-precipitated homicide or "suicide-by-cop." Parent proposed to conduct a "post-mortem psychoanalysis" on Yatim by examining a combination of: (1) SMS text messages between Yatim and a friend where Yatim expressed suicidal ideation; (2) a Google search history on Yatim's phone that included terms "the easiest way to kill

yourself," and; (3) a series of actions and interactions captured on surveillance videos that, for Parent, indicated Yatim was contriving a scene that would necessitate lethal use-of-force by responding officers. This paper discusses Parent's testimony in a voir dire admissibility hearing and the Judge's decision to bar Parent's testimony on the grounds that he neither had the relevant expertise nor was an expert opinion required to assess Yatim's 'state of mind' due to the availability, and 'common-sense' interpretability, of Yatim's conduct on video leading up to the shooting. This contributes to a broader discussion of how video evidence features in criminal trials for police officers accused in on-duty use-of-force incidents, where video evidence is largely circumstantial (as opposed to demonstrative) and arguments revolve around the 'state-of-mind' of either the victim or the accused.

Use Of Force Models: A Practice In Search of a Science *Albert Jay Meehan, Oakland University; AnnMarie Dennis, Oakland University*

In his classic treatise on United States policing, Egon Bittner (1970:37-38) observed that the lawful use of force by the police was "essentially unrestricted" by law and that instructions officers received about use of force largely amounted to "sermonizing" and "sanctimonious homilies" to be "humane and circumspect" in its practice of force. In the ensuing years, the landscape of police training has dramatically changed through the lamination of "science" onto the force decision-making process to provide post-hoc rationalizations of the "reasonableness" of the force decision. In this paper we examine two such changes: a) the development and evolution of use of force models (i.e., the "force continuum") within police training which we consider expert "mock-ups" (Garfinkel and Sacks 1970) of real-world situations that are understood by officers as merely having "resemblances" to actual situations but "inadequate" as a guide to practical action in any actual use of force and; b) the creation of "force science" as a new field which employs "unbiased scientific principles and processes to determine the true nature of human behavior in high stress and deadly force encounters" (<https://www.forcescience.org/>). The data are drawn from police training materials, trial testimony of officers and force experts in police deadly force cases, and videos of police-involved shootings.

Session Organizer:

Michael Lynch, Cornell Univ.

Discussant:

Mariana Valverde, University of Toronto

203. Diplomacy in a time of division, II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Ours is a time of division and fractures—a time of crises. Given the urgent problems we must face, there is no guarantee on predicting how will the agents involved, both human and other-than-human, will respond, let alone forcing one set of conditions upon them, or using them at will. In fact, we can only be certain of the divergence of obligations and requirements of the diverse parts involved (Stengers 2011). The unstable and heterogeneous landscape of current and urgent problems calls for a radically different role for scientific practices. Their aim is not to neutralize divergences, securing one expert consensual take, but rather these practices must take part in a heterogeneous and ecological assembly. If scientific practices, along with their experts, are not to be the great deciders, what role should they play? How should they behave? In what terms must they present themselves? This is the central problem of diplomacy, as Isabelle Stengers (2011, 2020) understands it. Diplomacy is a device to render different voices equal—not interchangeable, but equally present—in every decision. A diplomatic practice comes out from a group and does not necessarily seek a common ground. Yet, they are all but undefined. Our aim is to consider the political impact that different practices—related to ecological and social problems, multispecies conversations, methodological aspects of STS, or others—could have and how would they behave when rooted in diplomacy.

Participants:

Global intervention with no common ground *Agustín Mercado, Centro de Investigaciones Interdisciplinarias en Ciencias y Humanidades, UNAM*

If we consider that neutrality is not an option – something that seems plausible given the heterogeneity of the world that we live in – we are left with the necessity of building modes of thinking and acting that are not aimed for an unreachable ideal. This is what Isabelle Stengers strives for when she proposes her peculiar concept of diplomacy, a way of taking into account the plurality of other beings and their environment, which does not seek an absolute agreement, or even an ultimate common ground. What diplomacy seeks is a local articulation between groups and societies that not only have different interests, but also face different risks. However, our present times pose an important and unavoidable question, for they have brought about crises in which we are all directly and intensely implicated. In their complexity, these events manifest themselves in different ways which cannot be collapsed into a single imperative. The aim of this talk is to consider the tools for massive intervention, known collectively as geoengineering, that can be deployed in the face of these truly global events, such as climate change. These tools are not neutral, and the multiplicity of risks that they bring about when they fall into such a heterogeneous collective are unmanageable. In other words: how can a potentially irreversible global act present itself if we are willing to part with the idea of an objective decision in favor of a diplomatic practice?

Knowledge Generation, Legitimacy and Social Imaginaries in Citizen Science: Ornithology Cases from Turkey *Hazal Baytok, Université Paris-Sud/Paris Saclay*

Citizen science is the public participation in scientific research by gathering, submitting or analyzing data (Bonney et al., 2016). It allows saving time and money; and bridge the intellectual divide between formal science and people (Skarlatidou et al., 2019). However, the knowledge generation processes and the legitimacy of the knowledge generated through citizen science has been a concern (Bonney et al., 2014). In this paper, we explore the legitimacy issue through the lens of Mansell's (2013) framework through 2 detailed case studies from Turkey in the field of ornithology. Mansell provides a typology of knowledge systems with respect to authority as constituted or adaptive; and nature of knowledge as curated or ephemeral (Mansell, 2013). She highlights constituted authority as in formal science institution, and adaptive authority that relies on bottom-up knowledge generation processes. Regarding knowledge, she defines curated knowledge as long-term accumulated knowledge, and ephemeral knowledge for more immediate action (Mansell, 2013). This categorization allows for examining the transitions between traditional and non-traditional knowledge generation mechanisms, address the legitimacy concern and demonstrate how they coevolve to form social imaginaries. The case studies exhibit a deeper understanding of how knowledge is generated, shared and diffused; the critical actors and their relations that play a role in its legitimization, how these processes depend on the authority and nature of knowledge, as well as the motivations of participants. The results will be supplanted by preliminary results from a large survey among users and non-users of these platforms.

Growing catharsis in a lab: Psychedelic Social work in India around Psilocybe Cubensis. *Nagesh Anand, Woodpeckers Initiative Foundation; Sneha Bhati, Woodpeckers Initiative Foundation; Prakash Kumar, Woodpeckers Initiative Foundation*

Lory was sitting on the beach by herself after ingesting 3.3 grams of dried fungi, for the coming 5 hours Lory, a social worker working with childhood cancer patients for the past 5 years, took a beautiful journey of forgiveness, immense love, and empathy.

She felt one with nature and cried with her, understanding her pain. Conflicts and contradictions seemed to dissolve. She felt calmer, and later after a week Lory felt rejuvenated," All is empty within", Lory says. Psilocybe Cubensis AKA shrooms, magic mushrooms, golden tops, cubes, or gold caps belong to the fungus family Hymenogasteraceae and was previously known as Stropharia Cubensis. It is the most well-known psilocybin mushroom due to its wide distribution and ease of cultivation. Psilocybe Cubensis grows naturally in bovine pastures of Odisha, Kerala, Tamilnadu, Bihar, Chitwan in the Indian Subcontinent. This paper attempts to observe the effects of these psilocybin-producing fungi on front-line social justice workers in particular. Due to the immense caseload, the mental strain of social workers engaged directly with various social issues in India is very high. Interviews with these workers suggest higher burnout due to overburdening of cases, in some social workers, desensitization follows. The paper also explores the use of entheogenic fungi to self-manage burnout and desensitization in social workers, we aim to assess this through long-format in-depth interviews. The paper would also explore Psychedelic Social work as a self-managing, emancipatory, democratic, citizen science-centric biopolitical tool for societal change in unequal and uncertain worlds. The paper is being written by three social workers doing psychedelic social work in India.

Belonging to Both Science and Spirituality: The Rhetoric of Francis Collins and Sam Harris *Michelle Cowan, Texas Tech University*

In the U.S., binary worldviews have reified a two-party system in which political affiliation seems tied to particular scientific and religious beliefs. If approached through Burke's framework of identification through "pious" association (Burke, 1935; Davis, 2008; Hawhee, 2004), people's views of religion and science are dragged in opposite direction by tangles of rival associations. These days, an individual's position on a scientific finding may be inextricably associated with religious beliefs that might otherwise seem irrelevant. My presentation analyzes the rhetoric of two individuals who occupy positions on both sides of the science and religion divide: Dr. Francis Collins, the head of the National Institutes of Health, and Sam Harris, a popular cognitive neuroscientist. Both of these men profess a commitment to the scientific method and to spiritual practices, but they disagree about the role, if any, religion or personal spirituality has in scientific discourse. Interestingly, they each use similar tactics to simultaneously assert opposition and claim membership in both spiritual and scientific discourse communities. In a society where science is seen as the antithesis of religion, successful attempts at belonging in both discourse communities are particularly deserving of attention. If opinion and membership within a discourse community can be fluid—and citizens can see this fluidity in the rhetoric of figures they respect—then we can be more optimistic about the possibility of reaching across or even collapsing political, scientific, and religious binaries.

Session Organizers:

Juan Felipe Guevara-Aristizabal, Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana-Cuajimalpa, México

Agustín Mercado, Centro de Investigaciones Interdisciplinarias en Ciencias y Humanidades, UNAM

Chair:

Juan Felipe Guevara-Aristizabal, Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana-Cuajimalpa, México

204. Frontline Workers & Researchers Co-creating Knowledge in COVID-19 & the Overdose Crisis

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

With the onset of COVID-19, already existent overdose crises in Canada and the United States have been exacerbated. For almost a decade the drug market in both countries has become increasingly volatile. In 2017, the

Canadian Research Initiative in Substance Misuse (CRISM) developed twelve projects to address opioid-related research and program priorities nationally, one being “peer engagement.” As a result, the “People with Lived Expertise (PWLE) of Drug Use National Working Group” was developed and has been meeting monthly since 2018. While not developed from grass roots organizing, researchers, activists, and frontline workers from across Canada have worked together to create projects developed and enacted by PWLE. This has not been without challenges. When enacting a project where goals, interests, time, needs and institutional power are different between researchers and members, tensions are bound to arise. These challenges have only been exacerbated by COVID-19, where frontline workers have had to respond to an increasingly dangerous drug supply, a lack of institutional supports, as well as the loss of their colleagues and the people they support. In this roundtable, the researcher and several members of the working group discuss the challenges of co-constituting knowledge under prohibition and a pandemic. We invite researchers to come and hear from PWLE responding to dual crises: COVID-19 and the overdose crisis, and how researchers can better work with and support knowledge-making, while trying to enact change.

Presenters:

Natasha Touesnard, Canadian Association of People Who Use Drugs (CAPUD)

Sean LeBlanc, DUAL (Drug Users Advocacy League)

Brandi Abele, Canadian Association of People Who Use Drugs (CAPUD)

Matthew Bonn, CAPUD, SCS, St. Mary's College

Alexandra DeKiewit, Canadian Association of People Who Use Drugs (CAPUD)

Session Organizers:

Jade Boyd, British Columbia Centre on Substance Use;
Department of Medicine University of British Columbia

Alex G Betsos, British Columbia Centre on Substance Use

205. How to Read the How-to, Part III: Pedagogy of Relations

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Salomé Skvirsky (2020) defines the process genre, or “how-to”-ness, as “the sequentially ordered representations of making or doing something.” Moving beyond the question of replicability in experimentation (e.g., Collins 1985), we take inspiration from Skvirsky to invite submissions that explore aesthetic qualities of the how-to genre in knowledge-making practices. Specifically, we want to extend her analysis to scientific and social-scientific manuals. In thinking about objects like field guides, ethnographic textbooks, ecological surveys, personal research journals, archeological codes and conventions, we ask: what kind of affects, attachments and aesthetic experiences are produced and reproduced in the doing of science and through its representation in manuals? Skvirsky focuses on absorption, but we also invite papers that explore other feelings like boredom, love, anxiety, resentment, awe, etc. How are they enabled by the “how-to” genre of the manual? And how does this genre produce, reproduce, and disrupt relations, good or otherwise, between knowledge producers, objects of study, disciplines, institutions, and places? The manual is also a genre of theory seen in the exemplar of J. L. Austin’s *How to do Things With Words*, Bruno Latour’s *Science in Action: How to Follow Scientists and Engineers through Society* and, to a certain extent, in Kate Brown’s *Manual for Survival*. We therefore invite submissions that interrogate a “how-to” manual as an object of analysis, but also as a mode of STS analysis and theorization, or, better yet, written in the how-to genre itself!

Participants:

How to Learn Without a How-to *Panchompoo Wisittanawat*,
Vanderbilt University

I desperately wanted to have this how-to. When I was a child, my grandfather made us origami figures from his weekly Chinese newspaper. The biggest hit was a face that could stick out its tongue. I so wished to learn how to make that. My grandfather tried to teach me, and I tried very hard to learn, but our efforts

ended in (my) frustrations. I was frustrated because he would not tell me step by step how to make it. He would only show me. That was fine, until I got stuck somewhere, and didn’t get the immediate next step. When that happened, my grandfather would take over my piece, and showed me how to do it. He would not stop at that step, however. He would keep on until the piece was finished. I had to get another piece of newspaper and start over, and I would get stuck about the same place, and he would help again. I never learned how to fold a tongue-sticking face. I now look back to our interactions with a better understanding of how people teach and learn; some ways of learning emphasize observation (e.g., Correa-Chávez & Rogoff, 2009), and resist breaking things down in steps (Bakan, 1993/1994). In this paper, I recover how to create a tongue-sticking face from newspaper, and explore what a how-to for a tongue-sticking face looks like and what it assumes about learning, thinking and doing.

How to read an evaluation manual *Hilde Reinertsen, The TIK-centre, University of Oslo*

This paper is a reading of a prime specimen of the how-to genre: The so-called “Handbook of evaluation questions”, issued in 1981 by the Norwegian foreign aid administration. The handbook concerned how to write a good evaluation report – and how to ideally implement a system for aid evaluation, in which all aid projects were perfectly planned and monitored in order to enable high quality evaluation. The handbook’s approach was directly inspired by a strong social science critique of foreign aid, and sought to implement social science methods for ensuring a more self-reflexive and transparent aid practice through more systematic documentation – which in turn would make evaluation possible. This paper investigates this handbook to understand its envisioned genres of evaluation and systems of evaluability. In so doing, the paper develops the concept of ‘optics of evaluation’ as a means to analyse evaluation tools, methods, practices and infrastructures (Reinertsen 2016, 2018). If we consider evaluation a ‘technology of seeing’ (Pasveer 1992), what does this technology make us see? How does the optic itself contribute to transform the object it investigates? In probing these questions, the paper extends longstanding STS interests in scientific observation (Latour & Woolgar 1986, Daston & Galison 2007, Vertesi 2015). The paper anchors this discussion in the handbook: What is this document? How does its genre, style, and aesthetic enable a certain vision of an evaluable society? And how does the handbook expect its prescribed genre of evaluation to contribute to fulfilling this vision of evaluability?

Instructions and Instructed Actions in Training Data Collection for Machine Learning: The Case of Digital Contact Tracing for COVID-19 *Ben Berners-Lee, University Of California San Diego*

The present study centers on the instructions and instructed actions involved in the collection of training data for Private Automated Contract Tracing (PACT), a machine learning based digital contact tracing (DCT) program for COVID-19 that is designed to, using Bluetooth low energy (BLE) signals, detect a user’s proximity to other app users and notify users if they have been “too close for too long.” As analyses inspired by the expression “garbage in, garbage out” have demonstrated, the training data on which supervised machine learning systems are based is a relevant and under-recognized site in the social science of machine learning. In the tradition of ethnomethodology, the present paper considers the collection of training data as a site of instructions and instructed action, comparing two training scenarios. In the first scenario, a purpose-built app instructs users, in a step-by-step “how-to” manner, where to stand and how to hold their device. In the second scenario, users choose their position and are invited to describe their position and environment in their own words. As is revealed by an analysis of instructions and instructed actions reported in these datasets and other PACT documentation, testers engage with the “how-to” app as part of a community of practice and their contributions

constitute legitimate peripheral participation. The practical accomplishment of instructed action contributes to the community negotiation of an understanding of space, proximity and what BLE engineers call the “phenomenology of Bluetooth,” which then serves as a basis by which machine learning algorithms are operationalized for DCT.

“Zero to Hero in 120 Days”: How to Manufacture a Military Working Dog Team *Ashley Elizabeth Drake, University of Chicago*

This paper investigates how U.S. military working dog teams operate on principles that both reflect and run counter to the usual disciplining procedures found in military training manuals. Mentioned extensively in the very first War Dogs Technical Manual of 1943 (TM 10-396), military engineers valued the canine propensity to bond with a human partner above all other traits. The manual refers to this trait as the dog’s “willingness” and encourages handlers to use this emotional connection to their advantage in training. Dogs, these and subsequent manuals assert, are not just “machine[s] which can be requisitioned from inventory, pressed into service, and then returned to storage until needed at some future time” (U.S. Army 1976, 4), but are subjects that must develop a strong bond with their handler in order to operate as detection technology. Drawing on extensive archival research and 12 months of ethnographic fieldwork at Lackland AFB, this paper analyzes how the military encodes and enacts an interspecies affective relationship within the framework of acceptable “technostrategic discourse” (Cohn 1987). While certain aspects of this relationship, such as the desire for a “willing” dog, can be easily codified within training manuals, other aspects fall outside the scope of this discourse and can only be imparted through the experience of training with a dog. I argue that the decision to include or omit aspects of the desired dog-handler bond demonstrates the inherent representational capacity of these documents to account for and weaponize an affective relationship (Latour 2010).

Session Organizer:

Boyd Ruamcharoen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Chair:

Emma Pask, University of Chicago

206. Practices and Methods of Repair and Maintenance of Cultural Media - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

In recent years STS scholars have turned toward maintenance and repair as vital but overlooked responsibilities necessitated by our increasingly interconnected world. By foregrounding the banal – even boring – work of maintenance and repair, historians, theorists ethnographers, and others have exposed the constant effort that goes into preserving the functionality of everything from the vast sociotechnical assemblages of interstate highways to small, localized issues of personal comfort and bodily politics raised by air conditioning. Yet STS scholars have not yet made serious engagements with the maintenance and repair of cultural media, whose symbolic dimensions are typically left to media studies scholars. While interdisciplinary border crossings between STS and Media have increased, the wholesale digitization of media technologies demands that STS scholars contend with when, how, where, and why cultural media like paintings, radio, film and TV, games, and social media are repaired and maintained. This panel seeks to promote good relations between these two fields, bringing together questions of visibility and invisibility, labor, and innovation central to STS inquiries into repair and maintenance practices with questions of power and communication central to Media Studies.

Themes to be explored in this panel might include but are not limited to: 1. Preservation and conservation of media artifacts 2. Sociotechnical repair and maintenance in archival collections 3. Digitization and the maintenance of media access 4. Fan and user resistance and repair practices 5. Software maintenance and algorithmic repair 6. Repairing trust and truth in social

media 7. Maintenance, repair, and normalization

Participants:

Maintenance work of the Independent Movie Theater During Covid-19 *Sam Addison Ankenbauer, University of Michigan; Alex Jiahong Lu, University of Michigan*

Independent movie theaters have been part of the critical recreational infrastructure for close-knit patron communities. They afford culture sharing among community members through the distribution, curation, and dissemination of independent films, and the materiality of independent theater space also informs and shapes the bond and relations among the patron community. However, the COVID-19 pandemic led to the mandated closure of independent theaters and breakdowns of their symbolic and material effects in culture sharing and community engagement. In this light, we aim to investigate the socio-technical practices adopted by independent theaters in the hope of maintaining and repairing the symbolic and material aspects of independent theater space in the face of breakdowns. Building on the discourse analysis of news articles, theaters’ social media posts, and interviews with 18 independent theater personnels, we foreground how independent theaters’ attempted to repair the access and distribution of films as cultural media and maintain the relations within the patron community. Our results show that migrating to online space (including independent film distributors’ virtual cinema systems, social media platforms, and more) have become the go-to solution for independent theaters’ repair and maintenance work, which seemingly makes space for new forms of community engagement and media artifact distribution. Yet, we interrogate how the material complexity of how patrons and independent theater space interact is not mediated as a result of the repair and maintenance work. Our work contributes insights into the politics and challenges of maintaining and repairing cultural space and artifacts through the process of digitization.

Maintenance as Care: Care for Media Technologies in Time-based Media Art. *Dirk van de Leemput, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Maastricht University*

Museums of contemporary art face the challenge of conserving the unconservable. Time-based media works of art – that have duration, installation and the use of media technology as defining characteristics – include technologies such as the internet or televisions. Museums thus face obsolescence and technological change when they conserve these works. The maintainers who help museums to continue these technologies play a key role, yet are a neglected group in narratives about art, conservation or technology. In this paper, I propose to study the maintenance of the media technologies used in time-based media art as practices of care. Building on insights from maintenance and repair studies and feminist theories of care, I develop a framework for studying care practices around media technology that studies two dimensions: First, what is it the maintainers ultimately want to continue? Is it an artwork, the possibility of an art form, or the technology? Second, at what level do the maintainers direct their care? At the object, the object network of care or its ecosystem? I demonstrate this framework with the results of fieldwork conducted around Tate, London, on the care for CRT monitors (Nam June Paik) and the internet (Tate’s Intermedia Art project). By examining these two dimensions, I highlight the invisible labor of the maintainers and their role in conserving time-based media art, but I also show the affect and complex relations involved in their care. Above all, the paper shows the manifold ways in which the continuation of media technologies in museums depends on the care practices of maintainers.

Apparitions of Game History: Tracing Games at World’s Fairs and Expositions *Rebecca Rouse; Bobby Schweizer, Texas Tech University*

There is a rich history of games at World’s Fairs across three contexts: on display in anthropological exhibits and as

technological demos; handed out or available for purchase as souvenirs; and as amusements in recreation zones. We have attempted to return to the site of World's Fairs, only to find game artifacts that were displayed or sold are mostly gone while memories of play in these contexts exist only as traces. Though exhibited games and souvenir games have some documentation or material persistence, the games 'for play' prove more troublesome. There are references to these games in a range of ephemeral materials, but direct evidence is largely absent or yet to be discovered. This presentation explores how the categories of games on display, souvenir games, and games for play have survived in various forms. We examine how professional and amateur historians, preservationists, and scholars pass the evidence (or lack thereof) of these games on from generation to generation by performing the collective maintenance of memory. Examining this memory work as we seek to contribute to it ourselves opens up a host of related questions relevant to games. Our quest to find and maintain memories of games at fairs leads to a heightened awareness of what has been lost or remains yet to be uncovered. The function of games at World's Fairs—whether collected and displayed as objects or enacted as performances—echo many of today's uses and preserving their memory helps us envision how games can and should be valued in the future.

Data, Decay, and Insights: Business Intelligence as Repair Work *Ingrid Erickson, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University; Carsten Østerlund, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University*

If data are the background to the future of work, artificial intelligence (AI) is the predominant force active in the foreground. In the work of business intelligence (BI), namely the use of data analytics to illuminate invisible problems, confirm intuitive hunches, and fuel new ventures, the demand for real-time insights is putting increasing pressure on BI analysts to embrace augmented forms of insight generation, essentially incorporating new elements of AI-powered prediction into their practice. Building on an initial set of exploratory interviews with BI analysts from various industries, we find that BI praxis is a multi-faceted site of repair work—full of complexity and negotiation, situated workarounds, unpredictable patterns of interaction, and a shifting array of tools and infrastructures. As an analytical focus, repair helps us identify several important factors when addressing the relations, affects, and practices embedded in data-driven work. First, it emphasizes the cyclical nature of algorithmic work practices. In the case of BI, analysts constantly rotate through data, analysis, and presentation work, and in the process engage in the ongoing repair of dashboards, databases, outdated infrastructures, contextual details, and misunderstandings. Second, acknowledging the temporality of algorithmic systems raises important questions about how relationships between past and future are accomplished and maintained in specific sociomaterial entanglements. Finally, the work of extracting insights from data places BI analysts in a powerful organizational position as curators of organizational memory and facilitators of knowledge production; this implicates matters of organizational learning and control.

Session Organizer:

Alexander John Daniel Mirowski, Indiana University

Chair:

Marina Fontolan

207. Artificial Intelligence in global perspective: inequalities, changing relations, governance - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

This panel aims to generate comparative insights into the ways in which AI technologies are debated, developed, applied and governed around the world. Developments in AI, machine learning, and big data are transforming societies, the relationships of humans to each other, and

interactions with the environment. Simultaneously, the deployment of AI, AI-based robots and smart information systems takes place in a context of global inequalities and competition, as well as well differences in cultural values, political systems and scientific capacities. In this panel we welcome contributions that explore aspects of the following questions: (i) What role do global inequalities and differences play in terms of how AI systems are developed, used and discussed in different global contexts? (ii) Which region-specific and shared global challenges emerge with regard to the governance of AI, AI-based robots and smart information systems? (iii) What are the effects of AI technologies on issues related to equality, diversity, justice and inclusion/exclusion around the world? (iv) What are the implications of the global adoption and use of AI systems for STS, and the ways in which relations between humans, data, intelligent machines and the (social and natural) environment are conceptualised and governed? The panel invites conceptual, theoretical and empirical contributions from across the world, with a particular interest in perspectives from Africa, Asia, the Middle East, Central and South America as well Oceania. Contributions that explore transnational developments or the effects of the international transfer of AI technologies from Europe and Northern America are also welcome.

Participants:

Coming Out or Fleshed Out? The Biodeterminism of Facial Recognition Technologies *Eleanor DRAGE, The University of Cambridge; Kerry Mackereth, University of Cambridge*

In 2017, Stanford researchers Michal Kosinski and Yilun Wang released a study claiming that their deep neural network (DNN) could identify whether or not an individual was queer or straight. Their study was met with public outcry and condemnation on the basis that this tool could forcibly 'out' queer people and, in doing so, put queer individuals at risk of violence. It also provoked fears that the DNN could lend new legitimacy to discredited forms of scientific racism such as phrenology and physiognomy by claiming to be able to read sexual orientation from people's faces. We argue that biodeterministic ideas from racial pseudoscience underlie the way that the DNN purports to 'out' people. In order to explore how biodeterministic technologies map, label and categorise bodies, we explore how rather than forcing individuals to 'come out', the DNN fleshes out social perceptions about queer identity in the faces of the participants. In doing so, the DNN transforms individuals' complex social identities and self-(re)presentations into biologised, innate traits. We conclude that the prevalence of biodeterministic logics and techniques in AI must be urgently addressed because AI-enabled technologies may become the latest modality of biodeterminism following the debunking of the notion of the 'gay gene'. Rather than conflating different forms of oppression, we treat racialised and gendered biodeterminism as intersectional and co-constitutive in order to demonstrate how AI renders these logics meaningful with and through one another.

Algorithmic Fairness Across Contexts and Social Media: Do Americans Think Predictive Automation is Fair? *Emilio Lehoucq, Northwestern University*

As algorithms become pervasive, algorithmic fairness is an increasingly debated terrain. A growing literature focuses on policymakers, advocates, and researchers. We know less about laypeople's perceptions of algorithmic fairness. The literature on "public understandings" studies people's knowledge about science and technology, as well as how they evaluate scientific and technological practices. However, this scholarship has not examined attitudes toward algorithms. Using predictive modeling on survey data, this article explores individuals' perceptions about the fairness of predictive automation in criminal justice, finance, and the workplace. Extending the emerging literature on algorithmic fairness, this article argues that we should distinguish between factors associated with people's perceptions about the fairness of algorithms across contexts and others that are context-dependent. Among the factors that are important across contexts, this article suggests that social media is part of the cultural

environment in which people think about algorithms.

Cross-Cultural Sense-Making – Navigating Cultural Differences In Responsible Innovation Within AI *Gro Thorbjørn Berg Sørensen, Technical University of Denmark*

The responsible governance of artificial intelligence (AI) and its societal implications is a complicated undertaking and the complexity increases as different cultural perceptions of technology and ethics intersect in this effort. International cooperation on responsible AI is thus an act of navigating divergent cultural perspectives as well as navigating between fundamental differences and misunderstandings across cultures. This paper addresses this conundrum by investigating how the cultural context influences the meanings ascribed to AI and its perceived socio-ethical implications and how these meanings are enacted in governance processes, which in turn affect the cultural context reciprocally. Through a systematic literature review of extant scholarship in the field of cultural sense-making of innovation, the paper presents the framework of 'cross-cultural sense-making' as a methodological way to uncover the practices of defining, interpreting, and enacting culturally situated meanings of AI ethics into governance measures. The purpose of cross-cultural sense-making is to produce emic accounts of the divergent cultural perspectives in the innovation process. Possibilities and limitations of the framework will be illustrated in a comparative analysis of AI governance practices in China and in Europe. The paper advocates for the value of cross-cultural sense-making as a productive perspective in STS scholarship, particularly within the field of responsible innovation. It is argued that nuancing our understanding of the processes by which culturally situated knowledges are enacted internally and perceived internationally can promote a more informed and inclusive global cooperation on responsible AI governance.

Avatars in the Wild: A Transnational Project on UX and Conversation Design *Elizabeth Rodwell, University of Houston*

Voice assistant use and acceptance differs dramatically in the U.S. and Japan. While a 2019 study determined that 46% of Americans regularly use voice assistants like Alexa, Google or Siri for "searches and other commands" (Palanica et al., 2019), comparable studies of the Japanese market showed that a majority of the country had never used one of these tools. Frequent juxtapositions of these two countries in the literature on artificial intelligence makes this divergence particularly interesting. For example, attempts to understand the role of culture in robot fabrication have invoked mass-mediated histories to interpret relative comfort with particular categories of machines (e.g. Richardson, 2016; Robertson, 2007). While the U.S. is frequently cited for its discomfort with anthropomorphic AI, Japan's low adoption rate for voice assistants in contrast with its global leadership in Artificial Intelligence has called for further investigation, particularly as it concerns those whose job it is to persuade users of voice assistants' trustworthiness and utility. This paper presents the perspectives of usability (UX) researchers working on conversational/voice assistant development in two different companies – one in New York, and the other in Tokyo. I argue that despite sharing methods common to those working in UX and machine learning, employees of these companies are taking radically different approaches to "humanizing" their AI and overcoming reluctance on the part of potential customers to engage with voice assistants in business (NYC) or in the home (Tokyo).

Session Organizer:

Achim Rosemann, De Montfort University, UK

208. Rethinking Expertise: A New Look at Digitization and Decentralization II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Participants:

Construction Of A New Reality Through Datafication Of Healthcare Practices: The Case Study Of A Smart Infusion Monitor *Sruthy Gopal, University of Hyderabad, India*

Datafication of medical practices can be identified as a peculiar category within the increasingly relevant datafied healthcare field. Based on the background work in a startup company that develops an IoT-based infusion monitoring system, the presentation tries to bring forth the idea that re-mediation through 'smart' healthcare devices can make core-changes in medical practices alter practitioner's definitions about the quality of infusion therapy. With the digitisation of gravity infusions, the continuous flow is translated as the fall of discrete drops with reference to quantified time. For the nurse who understands fluid administration through intravenous infusion as a continuous flow of fluid over time, the device and the data generated through it create a reality built on the algorithm and database. It creates new understandings which can blur or mask existing functionalities. For instance, the errors in flow rate, which were not visible, come alive, where the time taken to resolve these errors could be considered a measure of "Quality". On the other hand, the machine also obscures the practitioner's awareness (of controllability) of the flow-rate. This new definition of "quality" is built based on the data generated from the device, captured, stored and interpreted through a designed structure called a time-series database. The presentation looks closely at the process of database architecture designing as devising a unique interface that lends the machine's interpretation of the process for human perception. The study's larger aim is to unpack the micro-processes of datafication as in an Actor-Network and to explore the scope of its domestication by sensitising the software engineer (designer).

Is All Technoscience Actually Value-Laden? A New STS Methodology for Studying Values in Expertise *Rowan Hildebrand-Chupp, UC San Diego*

The claim that "Science, technology, and medicine are always value-laden" is generally considered a truism in Science & Technology Studies. However, STS researchers often struggle to explain how a particular technology, classification, or expert decision is or becomes embedded with values. In a review of canonical scholarship in STS and the philosophy of science on the role of values in expertise, I find that scholars often claim that experts are influenced by "implicit," "tacit," or "hidden" values. However, these scholars do not provide any methodology for distinguishing experts' tacit assumptions about reality from their tacit values, and thus are unable to provide empirical evidence regarding how values operate in technoscience. I propose a new methodological approach for STS researchers to study values in technoscience that integrates methodological insights from cultural sociology with Actor-Network Theory in order to study values as actants. That is, by studying the rare moments where actors explicitly evoke values in justifications for a given position within a specific situation, STS researchers can trace these values to see whether they become instantiated in the form of the decision or object that is being assembled. In other words, rather than seeing values as hidden motivations, we should study values as actants that experts can enroll in order to craft positions in novel, unfamiliar situations. I conclude by discussing one striking implication of this approach: in an empirical sense, most technoscience is probably not embedded with values, even if processes of (e)valuation are involved.

Living With, Beyond And Despite Of Data: The Experiences Of Users And Non-Users Of Dietary Tracking Apps *Giada Danesi, University of St. Gallen; Tanja Schneider, University of St Gallen*

This paper draws on an interdisciplinary research project

“FoodCoach” aiming to make a research-based contribution to reducing diet-related diseases. The project develops an automated approach for analysing digital purchase data – collected and donated by volunteer users sharing their data collected through Swiss retailers customer loyalty programmes – and makes it available to their individual users in an easily understandable form via a digital app. Computer science and information management scientists, STS researchers and users collaborate in the project dealing with and intervening into the datafication of food consumption and the knowledge produced in the process. Social science research is being carried out to collect the lived experiences of users and the reservations of non-users towards digital nutrition monitoring and intervention. The data are collected through ethnographic methods, such as participant observations of and informal interviews with the various actors involved in the project and go alongs during food purchasing of users and non-users of self-tracking apps. The aim is to observe and discuss their experiences, practices and attitudes towards the collection, circulation and use of their food and health-related personal data. Our contribution will present the ways in which users and non-users choose to engage and to not engage with these data in the light of their needs, possibilities, interests and experiences. In analysing what the data means and what can be done with it by the different actors and from different perspectives, our intention is to unfold and discuss the multiple agencements at play in the ‘human-data assemblages’ (Lupton 2018).

Self-tracking Technologies and the Menstrual Cycle: Embodiment and Engagement with Lay and Expert Knowledge *Letizia Zampino*

The paper explores how humans intra-act with self-tracking technologies, reconfiguring the plurality of expert and lay knowledge. In particular, the current contribution presents an empirical analysis of the use of apps to manage menstrual periods. The article is positioned at the crossroad between three literatures: actor-network theory; new relational materialism; and a sociomaterial perspective on the medical field as relates to self-tracking practices. These approaches contribute to pay attention on the processes of embodiment and embodied knowing situated into sociomaterial practices. The aim is to explore how the body learns “to be affected” through the material entanglements between humans and apps, and how selftracking technologies are engaged and provide support for processes of embodied knowledge. Research findings draw attention to how interviewees intra-act with apps for menstrual tracking, along an imaginary continuum at whose opposite points we can find – on the one hand – minimal engagement with the knowledge inscribed in the app and – on the other – an affective engagement with the knowledge suggested by the app. This continuum shows the overlapping intra-actions that perform embodied knowledge about how women fertility, subordinate to the various historical stereotypes, works.

Structural Proximity: Relation between Inequalities and the Access to Reproductive Technologies among Ethnicized Groups *Safak Kilictepe, Kirsehir Ahi Evran University*

This paper illustrates in what ways political conflicts affect women’s access to reproductive technologies and shape their experiences with reproduction and motherhood desires differently within and outside of their own ethnic group. We have now come to know that both the geographic areas and imagined nation-states play significant roles in constructing individuals’ everyday experiences (Martin 1991; Massey 1994; Puar 2007; Radcliffe 1999). Both are important to reckon with when attempting to capture the fractured nature of everyday life. Hence, I suggest the term structural proximity as a tool to explain how and in what circumstances individuals become more vulnerable to politically changing environments, specifically in relation to the stratification of women’s reproductive experiences within changing conditions. I discuss that it is important to look

at women’s intersectional positionalities that are historically shaped, politicized, gendered, and class-based in order to understand the stratified aspect of reproductive experiences during and after political conflict. Thus, by focusing on Kurdish women’s position within their political and historical context, I expand upon “stratified reproduction” arguments to understand how changing politics shape reproductive experiences based on the situatedness of individuals within the power structure. This paper draws from my long-term ethnographic doctoral dissertation research on reproductive experiences of ethnicized Kurdish women living in Turkey. The research was carried out for seventeen months between 2016 and 2017 in the socio-culturally diverse capital Ankara (for five months) and the Kurdish populated metropolitan city Diyarbakır (for 12 months).

Session Organizer:

Emine Onculer Yayalar, Bilkent University

Chair:

Melike Sahinol, Orient-Institut Istanbul

Discussant:

Erkan Saka, İstanbul Bilgi University

209. Scaling the Ethical Plateaus of Energy Justice - IV

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Energy systems are in a state of flux. Climate change, the COVID-19 pandemic, the collapse of oil and destabilized energy economies have forced the world’s energopolitical regimes (Boyer 2019) to grapple with new and evolving demands on and for energy infrastructures. These geopolitical shifts signal both emerging windows of opportunity and causes for concern, as the ethical plateaus that have come to define contemporary energy ecologies rupture at their fault lines. The growing set of diverse conceptual complements with which energy is often paired (e.g., energy rights, energy vulnerability, energy democracy, energy transitions, etc.) betray different assumptions about the scales and systems of relevance to energy politics and to processes of sociotechnical change. Energy justice, by contrast, calls for a more holistic view of the ethics informed by unique energy ecologies—i.e. the historically and culturally specific modes of relating to one’s self, to other humans, to non-human life, and to the environment through one’s relationship to energy and energy infrastructures. This means that more nuanced attention is needed to account for and enact just energy relations in situ. Session #4 “Legacies of Petrocapitalism” includes papers that critique petrocapiatalism and its continued power to shape contemporary and/or emergent energy systems.

Participants:

Energy Justice Against Disaster: On Climate Change, the Texas Grid, and Disjointed Energy Ecologies *James Adams, University of California, Irvine*

This paper takes the recent 2021 Texas blackouts as a case study of the disjointed energy ecologies of grid disasters. Energy ecologies are here conceived as tangles of environmental, biological, technological, social, and mental processes, each with their own speeds, durations, and syncopations, where rhythms and cycles intersect, attenuate, synchronize, and feedback across the full gamut of socio-natural scales and systems. Disaster scholars taught us to pay attention to disasters’ slow/fast temporalities, and to value diverse temporal scales of disaster research. Building on this work, I intend to open up a different analytical space for time within disaster studies, shifting from the temporality of disasters to considering disaster itself as emergent from a given ecology’s disjointed temporalities. Whether discussing fuel-source intermittency, load frequency control, real-time markets, or emergency response times, the synchronization of speeds and intensities is the essential resiliency challenge of the Texas grid. And, comparatively, Texas grid operators have been relatively well-equipped and successful in this domain. However, climate change, aging infrastructure, emerging technologies, and shifting cultural values are getting ahead of these formerly effective systems of

control. Recently, as polar storms rolled across Texas, over 4.5 million Texans lost power, resulting in at least 30 deaths and an estimated \$200 billion in damages. These blackouts are paradigmatic of Texas' fraying energy ecology and fractured ethical plateaus. In this paper, I critique the Texas grid's structuration of petrocapiatist temporalities, identifying avenues for a simultaneous de/re-synchronization of this ecology around the values and temporalities of energy justice and democracy.

In Situ: Energy, Heritage, and Archaeology in Arkadia, Greece
Nathaniel T Stanton, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute - STS

'Arcadia' is best known not as a place but as a metaphor for bucolic paradise, but in actuality, Arkadia is a Greek province facing an uncertain future. Arkadia emerged as an important resource periphery of Greek modernity in the 1950s when lignite coal was discovered in the plains surrounding the town of Megalopoli. By the late 1960s, this lignite provided power for all of Southern Greece and, subsequently, lignite mining and burning became central to Arkadian identity. Today, the area is an ecologically-destroyed moonscape with dwindling reserves, but lignite production continues. In reaction to European Union climate regulation, the government plans to close lignite facilities by 2023. The local community, concerned about negative economic impact, have protested this closure but ultimately have little agency in a newly liberalized energy market. However uncertain, Arkadia's future is marked with the hope that lignite's death may give way to new life via archaeological and natural landscape heritage. New government plans to cover the mountainous terrain with wind parks and solar panels, however, place Arkadia's sustainable heritage and tourist future at risk. Marshaling participant observation, ethnographic data, and historical analysis, this paper will introduce the concept of "crypto-colonialism" (Herzfeld 2002) to Post-Colonial STS approaches, and further engaging with critical studies of infrastructure, extraction, heritage and archaeology, to offer theoretical insight into the production of Arkadian subjectivity and futurity, torn between underground resource extraction, archaeological excavation, mountainous landscape beauty, a history of resistance, and potential manipulation into yet another future as energy periphery.

Moral rifts in the coal phase-out — How mayors navigate and constrain distribution and recognition for a "just transition" in Lusatia
Jeremias Herberg, Institute for Science in Society, Radboud University; Konrad Gürtler, IASS Potsdam

Phasing out coal production and consumption in Europe and Northern America implies is a broad, but highly selective renegotiation of energy justice. The discourse about so-called "just transitions" – triggered by trade unions as well as policy makers – is restricted to resources that are largely detached from, and unavailable to the communities that are most vulnerable to climate change. What are the justice debates and policy practices that structure and facilitate a geographically selective view on the moral dimensions of socioecological transformations? This contribution explores how justice demands that range from distributional, recognition-based to procedural aspects interact within and fold into socioecological transformations within Northern European industrial regions. Based on qualitative inquiries in Lusatia, Germany, we show how policy makers navigate and seek to reconcile contradictory justice demands. We argue that the notion of 'moral rifts' can shed light on possible interactions within the European coal phase out, stressing the situatedness and moral selectivity of local transformations. We highlight the political and cultural legacies of fossil fuels, the post-socialist experience and the friction between energy production and consumption as moral rifts. Mayors navigate those rifts, and thereby foreground the competition for resources that are mostly unavailable to less privileged regions. We close with a discussion on the connection between moral rifts and right wing populism in European coal regions.

Petrochemical Infrastructures in Transition
Sonia Grant, Dalhousie University

This paper explores one dimension of a tumultuous energy transition unfolding in Dinéah, where tribal and state governments are grappling to diversify energy sources and economies in order to become less reliant on coal, oil, and gas. I draw on long-term ethnographic research with Diné people in Eastern Navajo Agency. Attending to an aspect of transition that is of particular concern to communities who have been living with extractive industries for centuries in the heart of a once bustling oil and gas field, I ask: what happens to decaying infrastructures whose products are no longer wanted? Thousands of the oil and gas wells densely scattered across Dinéah are on the brink of abandonment. As pollutants continue to seep out from deserted wells, the land cannot be used in other ways by Diné people. Watchdog groups and governments increasingly recognize that existing bonding requirements for the oil and gas industry fall woefully short of covering the costs of plugging wells and remediating lands. This imbalance is leading to a crisis of responsibility for addressing infrastructural detritus and the cumulative social and ecological impacts from oil and gas extraction, raising important questions for what restorative energy justice might mean. This paper outlines the American financial and administrative logics that make places like Dinéah vulnerable to infrastructural abandonment and its associated colonial violence. Thinking with Diné colleagues who are advocating for a "just energy transition", I posit the working out of non-extractive land relations as a crucial component of an anti-colonial energy politics.

Session Organizer:

James Adams, University of California, Irvine

210. Psychoanalysis and STS Meetup

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

Psychoanalysis, as practice and as theory, has a complicated relationship with STS. Those of us either interested in this intersection - or working within it - seem to be relatively isolated between institutions. Building off of a successful panel at the 2020 meeting, this meetup is proposed to offer a place for those of us working with psychoanalytic theory within STS - or vice versa - a place to gather, share our work, and create some theoretical community with the 4S organization!

Session Organizer:

Jamie Steele, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Chair:

Jamie Steele, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

211. Unpacking the "datafied" society: shifting politics of seeing and knowing - I: Critical Reflections On Datafication

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Participants:

Assessing the Value of a Home: Lessons from a data initiative for training data scientists' ways of seeing and knowing
Margarita Boenig-Liptsin, Human Contexts and Ethics Program, Division of Computing, Data Science, and Society, UC Berkeley; Ari Edmundson, Human Contexts and Ethics Program, Division of Computing, Data Science, and Society, UC Berkeley; Anissa Tanweer, 2511 NE 165th St; Stephanie Shipp, University of Virginia; Micaela Parker, Academic Data Science Alliance; Anna-Maria Gueorguieva, UC Berkeley; Carlos Ortiz, UC Berkeley; Eva Newsom, UC Berkeley

In 2018, Cook County Assessor's Office launched an open data project to make the housing assessment process more transparent to residents. The Office has been the subject of revelations and lawsuits that its assessment practices were placing a

disproportionate tax burden on homeowners in lower income and predominantly Black neighborhoods. We analyze this project by breaking down decisions involved in the design of the system according to the stages of the data science lifecycle and analyzing each stage with key STS theoretical concepts (positionality, power, narratives, and sociotechnical system). Our analysis reveals how governments can use data in pursuit of justice by shaping the community's ways of seeing and knowing. The result is a system that operationalizes an idea of justice-as-fairness at a moment in time when groups fighting for racial justice around the world are advocating for a conception of justice beyond the distributively fair. This case study offers lessons for training future data scientists. By breaking down the data project according to the data lifecycle stages and analyzing each stage with the STS concepts we develop a tool to train the next generation of data scientists to reflect on the human and ethical contexts of their profession and practice. This paper thus not only offers an analysis of how the politics of seeing and knowing is shifting in the datafied world, but presents a normative intervention of how to shape this shift with STS frameworks.

Computing the Social: How Commodified Data in AI Shapes Perceptions Of the World *Onurhan Ak, Queen's University, Department of Sociology*

Scholarship has examined the politics of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in terms of its consequences for social inequities as well as the expertise, practices, and cultures of its development. However, research has paid little attention to the epistemological implications of the economic nature of big data that is used in development of AI: because AI development requires large data sets, this data often comes from platforms which collect it for purposes of monetization – it is hence commodified data. This paper explores how commodified data shapes conceptualizations of the social in AI research in Canada in the context of the COVID-19 pandemic. How is the social conceptualized in AI work? What kind of societies are imagined? What are its basic units? How do they relate to each other and what kind of structures govern their relationships? What kind of realities are enacted and what kind of possibilities are foreclosed as a result? I will present preliminary findings from in-depth interviews with AI researchers who work on public health issues in Canada's AI labs. By exploring these questions, I seek to better understand how the political economy of data shapes how we relate to the world in AI, and the potential implications of this when AI systems are used in governance.

Data Inquiries Critical Data Practice in the Classroom *Tommaso Venturini, CNRS; Jonathan Gray*

While data literacy is considered a key competence in higher education curricula, its teaching often focuses on technical skills, rather than engaging with the social lives and sociotechnical infrastructures of data. Trained on artificial exercises and mock-up datasets, students are not exposed to the richness and messiness of real-life data practices and disregard "the other 90% of data science" (Dumitand&Nafus, 2019). Conventional training reinforces a naively technical approach to data literacy. Students assimilate techniques of analysis and visualization, but fail to learn the subtler crafts of examining issues with and about data. Despite the growing literature on critical data studies from feminist, postcolonial, security, and STSs, many curricula continue to skip over the reduction and transformation associated with datasets production. To promote a more thoughtful and realistic approach to "data literacy", researchers affiliated with the Public Data Lab (publicdatalab.org) have experimented with a different pedagogical approach. Reviving Dewey's social inquiries, the PDL has promoted situated learning experiences with civil society groups. This included research on online misinformation with fact-checkers; on international finances with tax campaigners; on societal engagement around forest fires with NGOs; on migration stories with social activists; on air pollution with city-planners; and on online public debates with

municipalities. This proposal provides a first explicit account of "data inquiries" as a pedagogical method, examining the classroom as a site of critical technical practice, exploring the organisation of group work, worksheets, work rhythms, reading lists, class schedules, evaluation formats, and cooperation outside the academia.

Toward Intimate Data: Re-thinking digital, social, political relations *Preston Welker, University of Calgary; Ryan Burns, University of Calgary; Anna Lauren Hoffmann, The Information School, University of Washington*

Digital technologies enable the mass datafication of human activity in new and intimate ways, allowing for both active and passive tracking bodily functions, physical movements, consumption habits, social encounters, and even moods and feelings. Despite the seeming newness of these developments, however, STS scholars recognize that data production and use has always been bound up with broader relations between individuals, communities, and claims to the privateness or publicness of certain bodies, spaces, and behaviors. Most recently, critical data scholars have illuminated the complex, often surreptitious contexts in which datafication occurs, offering a range of conceptual frameworks to contend with the meanings and implications of these deeply personal digital-human entanglements. In this paper we take up and recast the notion of "intimate data." Elsewhere denoting a particular category of tracked activities deemed private or sensitive, we instead consider intimacy as marking a set of (often unequal) socio-political relationships. That is, we mobilize "intimate data" to attend to the processes by which individuals and collectives are datafied in ways that have repercussions for knowledges about oneself and others. In so doing, we sidestep hermetic liberal conceptions of data that center ideals like consent and exchange to think about data collection as eliciting confessions, vulnerabilities, monetizable practices, and new possibilities for governing (inter)personal and other relations. We advance different, alternative political responses, focusing specifically on (1) the (racialized, gendered, classed, sexualized) normativity of intimate data, (2) (re)considerations of privacy and surveillance, (3) tensions around visibility, and (4) responsabilization of individuals to police spaces.

Towards a post-abysal data ethics *Catriona Gray, University of Bath*

Boaventura de Sousa Santos has developed the concept of abyssal thinking to describe a colonially instituted system of distinctions through which social reality is effectively divided in two, with one side rendered invisible, absent and non-existent. Abyssal thinking grants to science a monopoly on the universal true/false distinction. Incommensurable forms of knowledge are vanished as irrelevant. The colonial zone, including its ways of knowing, is rendered a realm of incomprehensibility and lawlessness resulting in a radical absence of humanity. This model, which prevails in modern Western thinking, is based on an innate sense of superiority and ownership over the entire world. Colonized and indigenous peoples and their lives are understood only as objects of knowledge, and never as contributors. I explore how the adoption and design of data-driven AI may reproduce and encode abyssal thinking. Forms of knowledge which do not fit with the modern scientific paradigm (e.g., beliefs, intuitions, and embodied and practical forms of knowledge) are radically excluded or, at most, provide the "raw" material in the form of input data. One of the most commonly cited advantages of AI technologies is their ability to "see" things that were previously invisible. I call for a decolonial interrogation of this claim, asking: what are the necessarily co-present invisibilities, and for whom is this "seeing" really a form of knowledge at all? I explore the potential of applying Santos' notion of ecology of knowledges in pursuit of a more emancipatory data ethics.

Session Organizer:

Bidisha Chaudhuri, International Institute of Information Technology Bangalore

212. Technologies of Death and Dying at the Beginning of Life - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

The advancement of reproductive technologies has not only made an impact on how life emerge; technologies also remake death and dying at the beginning of life. In fertility clinics surplus embryos raise questions regarding if, when, and how they can be discarded or used for non-reproductive means. Ultrasonography used for prenatal diagnosis situate expecting parents in situations of whether they should terminate the pregnancy when fetal malformations are detected, and infants some time die even though technologies are used to keep them alive. Moreover, new technologies are developed in regards to handling dead bodies. This includes post-mortem diagnostics or the development of cooling technologies, such as the cooling cot, a technology that may enable new bereavement practices. In this panel, we welcome presentations that explore in which ways technologies are part of death and dying at the beginning of life around the globe, by asking: How are technologies of death and dying regulated, practiced and lived with? How do technologies impact when a life is deemed killable and grievable? How do processes and conceptualizations of death and dying alter as technologies are increasingly involved in reproduction? How do parents or the medical staff involved, live with the deaths that emerge with technologies? And what are the theoretical implications of rethinking technologies of life to also focus on technologies of death? Finally, we welcome reflections on the politics of ontology, and conceptualizations of technologies of dying, as death at the beginning of life is explored. Potential topics include: technologies of death and dying, grief, infant death, abortion, reproductive technologies

Participants:

The deficiency of human reproductive biology in fertility treatment practices *Elina Helosvuori, Tampere University*

In a glossary definition, infertility is defined by 'failure' to achieve a clinical pregnancy within a certain time frame. Fertility treatments are conducted to enable otherwise unlikely or impossible pregnancies. As shown by previous reproductive studies, especially in vitro fertilization (IVF) has established its place as the hope technology par excellence in the field of reproductive desires. However, a paradoxical feature of the broadening possibilities of human reproduction is that when healthy people take part in clinical practices of procreative interventions, their reproductive systems become classified according to medical professionals' perception of them as either normal or deviant. Based on a multi-sited ethnography conducted in Finland, I explore how IVF is practiced and lived through not only as a technology of creating life, but also a platform for reproductive disappointments, as well as cellular and embryonic death. I examine the 'fragmentation of the body' that is characteristic of current biomedicine, as discussed by Nikolas Rose. Deepening the analysis of the process of fragmentation in the case of assisted reproduction, I argue that through developments in biomedicine and the transnational fertility industry: through clinical and laboratory practices, the biological markers of (in)fertility and the deficiency of human reproductive biology become increasingly numerous and specific. By implication, also personal experiences of cellular and embryonic death, and pregnancy losses after IVF are translated into feelings of embodied failure and deviance.

Laying to rest: The legitimation work in 2nd trimester abortion for medical reasons in Denmark *Laura Louise Heinsen, AC Meyers Vænge 15, 2450, Copenhagen SV*

In this paper, I present findings from my ongoing ethnographic PhD research on the legitimization, authorization, and effectuation of 2nd trimester abortion for fetal anomaly in Denmark. Through accounts of women, men and couples who had opted for termination following the detection of a fetal

abnormality, I examine the language with which such terminations are depicted, as well as the intimate domestic spaces and material objects of grief and memorialization that people use to legitimate and live with their decision. In my talk, I will show how termination is ambiguously configured both as abortion of a futile fetus and as killing of a precious baby to be birthed, seen, held and mourned. Building on Sonja van Wichelen's concept of legitimation work as 'enactments of ethics' (2019), I develop a framework of 'laying to rest' to illustrate the morally and emotionally troubling process of legitimating both the decision to choose termination and the experience of termination as infant loss, one that, I argue, is continuous, iterative and never-finished. The paper aims to contribute to current STS and anthropological studies of reproductive technologies by bringing fetal death and its sociotechnical shaping to the center of analysis.

Shadows Of Absence: Ultrasound As A Technology Of Death In The Lothians, Scotland. *Tara Pollak, The University of Edinburgh*

Well known research on 'ordinary' pregnancy (Davies-Floyd 1992, Han 2013) and 'risky' pregnancy (Casper 1998, Rapp 1999) shows that ultrasound is a technology that is medically, socially and emotionally significant. In this paper, I explore how ultrasound produces anxiety, grief and helplessness and how it sheds light on disruptions and potentials for kinship and care. My doctoral research with bereaved families in the Lothians, Scotland found that anticipated scans become an unwanted diagnosis and the availability of private ultrasound clinics a dreaded option in an overburdened health care system. During Covid-19, ultrasound appointments are guarded, with those previously promised additional scans or experiencing symptoms of miscarriage having to wait for their scheduled appointments. Some families seek out commercial ultrasound clinics in an attempt to find reassurance. In the hands of an unregulated profession with no authority to diagnose, parents are offered keyrings and mugs instead of support. The back and forth between private clinics and public health care indicates how ultrasound is a wanted technology, even at the prospect of unwanted news. This unwantedness however, may still hold reproductive potential in the form of kinship and relevant medical information. By reconfiguring ultrasound as a technology of death, characterised by reproductive absences, disruptions in care and support become visible, compounding families' experiences of loss. At the same time, parents' engagements with ultrasound and its information produces avenues for improved biomedical care, community support and kinship in Scotland.

Uncertain Imaginaries. Prenatal testing, late-term abortion and the potentialities of a life (not) worth living *Veronika Siegl, University of Cologne*

This presentation explores how "lives (not) worth living" are negotiated in the context of late-term abortions on embryopathic grounds in Austria. As in many other countries, abortions after the first trimester in Austria are only authorized from case to case, for instance, when the foetus is assumed to be "severely damaged". Since the law does not define "severe damage", individual physicians and hospitals have to develop their own moral standards – a responsibility which can be perceived as a burden, but which also entails considerable power in defining "lives worth living". However, decisions about which abortions to approve and which not, always rest on uncertain grounds. As diagnoses are seldom absolute and certain, doctors and other decision-makers have to rely on medical technologies to try to imagine or predict what a child's life will look like. The lack of clear legal criteria in Austria also results in massive differences between hospitals and "abortion tourism" within the country, mainly to the capital, where doctors have to perform the emotionally burdening "dirty work" for the entire country, as some of them say. Against this background, my presentation explores the different medical "landscapes" in Austria and seeks

to understand how doctors, geneticists and obstetricians make use of and speak about medical technology when trying to imagine future lives and when making existential decisions regarding un/born “life” in a setting of high uncertainty and legal vagueness.

Session Organizer:

Stine Willum Adrian, Aalborg University

Chair:

Anna Sofie Bach, Aalborg University Copenhagen

213. Interrogating the Unicode Project: Language, Design, and Identity

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

The Unicode Standard serves as the technical backbone for text encoding and gives proper form to most of the world’s writing systems on contemporary digital platforms. Among other features, Unicode contains specifications for over 140,000 individual characters (letters, ideographs, punctuation marks, and symbols), along with basic information required for rendering emoji. Like any other technical system, Unicode is built and run by interested social actors, in this case The Unicode Consortium, an American nonprofit with membership composed of big tech companies, other nonprofits, and even ordinary people drawn to the Unicode project. It is no exaggeration to say that modern multilingual computing and communication technology would not exist in the forms they take today without Unicode. That said, Unicode presents both significant opportunities and challenges to users of digitized writing systems, especially scripts for minority languages that have been overlooked by various power-brokers. This panel introduces the Unicode project as a subject of scholarly inquiry from a range of STS vantage points. What makes technical material so difficult to understand? What work is being done to bridge the interests of technical actors and user communities, and what resources does this require? What motivates these boundary actors in the realm of writing systems? And how are peripheral communities in the Global South assigning meaning to and negotiating with these standards?

Participants:

An Illustrated Guide to Unicode *Jonathan Soma*, *Columbia University*

Who said a 1000+ page technical document has to be boring? We'll go on an interactive journey through the history and foundations of Unicode: discovering how computers learned to read, why cut-and-paste doesn't always cooperate, and what flat-heeled shoes have to do with international standards. The road to a worldwide standard for digitizing text began in the 1960's and is still continuing today. Each step along the way is its own intersection of technical limitations and often-flawed human decision-making, creating historical and cultural artifacts that impact us each time we send an email or annotate a document. We'll step through that history and see just how the technical tendrils of the past reach out to us today.

Bridge Over Troubled Waters: The Script Encoding Initiative as an intermediary between Unicode and digitally-disadvantaged language communities *Isabelle Zaugg*, *Columbia University*, *Data Science Institute*, *Institute for Comparative Literature and Society*

Unicode’s role in opening the digital sphere to users of diverse global languages has only begun to be recognized by scholars and the wider public. But how have Unicode’s structures and policies shaped its support for the world’s most digitally-disadvantaged scripts and languages? This paper draws on interviews, archival research, and institutional observation of Unicode and its partner institution, ISO Subcommittee 2, I began carrying out as part of my dissertation research in 2014. Lessons learned from these organizations’ strategies for working with digitally-disadvantaged script/language communities can inform efforts by a growing number of digital governance institutions to widen linguistic access to the digital sphere. In particular, the

role of the non-profit Script Encoding Initiative (SEI) as an intermediary between script communities and the highly technical world of Unicode, is one characterized by “good relations.” SEI acts as a human face and an expert guide during the process of developing a proposal that contains all the details of a script’s workings, a document required for Unicode and ISO 10646 encoding to move forward. SEI’s work includes addressing communities’ concerns about corporate “control” of their script, and using diplomatic approaches to lobby for government approval of scripts used by minority groups within their borders. SEI facilitates a technical process through systems marked by corporate, government, and user-community power by building trust and relationships. This paper investigates SEI’s largely hidden yet essential, ongoing role in creating a bridge between digitally-disadvantaged script communities and the digital sphere.

Caring for Writing *Keith Murphy*, *UC Irvine*

Graphic language—including writing systems, character sets, typefaces—is a regular feature of the everyday world. One implication of this endemic regularity is that the “invisible technicians,” to borrow Shapin’s phrase, who create and maintain graphic language systems assume significant responsibility for ensuring that visible language actually “works” as language users expect it to, in very fine-grained detail. Since early 2019, I’ve been conducting ethnographic research in New York and San Francisco with several groups of these invisible technicians. One of the most critical of these communities is the Unicode Consortium, and in particular the Script Ad Hoc Committee, a group of mostly self-selected language and technology experts who guide the process of encoding under-represented scripts to make them useable with modern technologies. These are people who truly care about — and care for — the details of glyphs, and the functionality of those glyphs, within technical and aesthetic systems. And yet, there is a certain melancholic irony to their work in the current moment: urban, Western technicians worrying the small details of script infrastructures while the big stuff — subways, water systems, electrical grids — are literally deteriorating around them. In this talk I’ll explore “caring for writing” and its smallest details in the shadows of late-capitalist America. I’ll analyze the tensions and rewards that Unicode members experience in taking care of tiny infrastructures—often for people they have no connection to—even while it feels like the world they’re working to support is collapsing.

The Case of the Missing Character *Anushah Hossain*, *UC Berkeley*, *Energy and Resources*

In late 2000, an email was sent out to the Unicode Consortium mailing list asking about the missing Bengali character khanda ta. The initial email regarding khanda ta received a reply saying it was an infrequently used symbol and could arguably be represented through complex combinations of existing symbols within the Unicode Standard. It was therefore unnecessary to include. The missing character khanda ta would go on to become a decade-long discussion between members of the Unicode Consortium; Bengali-computing volunteers from Bangladesh, West Bengal, and the diaspora; and occasional institutional interlocutors from industry and the Bangla Academy. Using ethnographic and archival methods, I trace the symbolic importance of the khanda ta character to these stakeholders, and what it illuminates about the politics of nationalism and language in the digital age. While the character was an example of technical redundancy and mob-mentality for its detractors, it came to represent the need for preservation and completeness of the Bengali identity in the digital environment for its proponents. Eventually, khanda ta was encoded — a singular victory for Bengali-computing volunteers — but persists as a meme and mistake in the minds of Unicode members. This project is ostensibly about Bangladesh, the Bengali language, and its script, but this case bears similarity to many post-colonial states who’ve sought to establish their national identity in the digital

environment. More broadly, it engages with questions of how and whose values are embedded in code, and what factors can cause those values to shift.

Session Organizer:

Anushah Hossain, UC Berkeley, Energy and Resources

214. Forensic Evidence And Expertise In Local, National And Global Contexts - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Forensic evidence is collected, analysed and rendered meaningful by different actors using various technologies and expertise. A powerful resource in the investigation of crime, STS scholars have paid substantial attention to the development, standardisation, enactment and use of specific forensic technologies (namely fingerprinting and forensic DNA profiling). These accounts demonstrate the complex expertise and labour involved in producing and using forensic evidence, and the many local and national contexts that impact on how the legitimacy and value of specific types of forensic evidence are negotiated over time. Beyond fingerprinting and DNA, there are many other types of forensic evidence. Some have long histories, like fibre analysis. Others, such as digital forensics, are newer and continually evolving, keeping pace and responding to the latest technological developments. In this panel, we invite papers that examine empirically the varied actors, labour and expertise involved in the production and use of other types of forensic evidence in the investigation and prosecution of crime. We are particularly interested in accounts that engage with how forensic evidence and expertise are negotiated in specific local, national and/or global law enforcement contexts and the related areas of overlap and convergence. This panel contributes to STS scholarship on the intersections between science, law and law enforcement, standardisation in scientific practice, and the negotiation of expertise across the different epistemic cultures of criminal justice systems.

Participants:

‘The long journey from resistance to acceptance’ – accrediting digital forensics practices in England and Wales *Dana Wilson-Kovacs*, University of Exeter

This paper explores the issue of standardisation through the lens of accreditation processes in digital forensic (DF) in policing in England and Wales. It focuses on the role and place of DF expertise and how this is imagined, presented and reflected upon by practitioners, police officers and regulators. The paper examines how those working in and with 4 DF units affiliated to four police forces in England reflect on the suitability of ISO17025, the impact of its introduction on existing protocols and wider practices surrounding the production of evidence for criminal justice purposes, and the accompanying organisational process of implementation. The analysis considers the journey from the resistance to the acceptance of standards through (1) ethnographic observations surrounding two UKAS accreditation visits, (2) and interviews with DF experts, DF practitioners and police officers over three years of the implementation process. It contributes to STS scholarship on forensics, evidence and expertise, and wider discussions elsewhere on responsibility, professionalisation and the use of forensic evidence in criminal investigations.

Making DNA Matter *Mareile Kaufmann*, Universitetet i Oslo

Evidence is a promise in the uncertain worlds of crime control and security politics. It is a promise to be kept by the means of scientific method. Especially in forensics, DNA analysis has long been considered a gold standard. Though STS scholarship has already called this status into question, DNA’s association with taken-for-granted scientific reasoning is persistent. In fact, expectations towards DNA and its analysis are reinvigorated now that both are increasingly integrated with digital technologies. New techniques include DNA sequencing at the crime site, phenotyping and the use of these extracted characteristics to make identikit pictures. In addition, the increasing number of DNA databases constantly provide new data to be analysed. This

digitization of DNA is not just a matter of societal, legal and ethical concerns, but digital technologies more fundamentally shape DNA evidence. They are methodical devices that neither render DNA into a new digital standard, nor into post-truths, but make DNA matter in new ways. This paper makes two contributions to STS scholarship. It develops a framework of ‘Making Information Matter’, which considers the lives and liveliness of all elements involved in the ongoing materializations that we study and are part of. It then applies this framework to the specific case of DNA to explain how it matters and is made to matter in the context of digital forensics. It traces the relations between scientists, digital devices and biological information, and shows how all of them become lively as they make DNA matter together.

Training Trust: Negotiating Machine Learning in Forensic Analytics in Criminal Prosecution *Katja Mayer*, Vienna University; *Sofie Kronberger*, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies

The increasing volume and variety of digital data and potential evidence is complicating investigations in law enforcement. Forensic analytics enhanced by machine learning (ML) emerged as a possible solution to inefficiency and delays. Automated sorting and classification of seized materials based on learning models should help investigators to better organize and manage evidence, and by now form the necessary basis for all further information retrieval and analysis. Moreover, these learning tools blur the established boundaries between forensic, investigative, and judicial processes and require the (re-)negotiation of trust, authority, transparency, and responsibility in the interaction between humans and machines. Drawing from an ongoing interdisciplinary research project at the intersection of law enforcement, machine learning and STS, we aim to interrogate the complex socio-technical relations of these new forms of knowledge production and the shaping of evidence. In our contribution we briefly map conflicting visions of trust, agency and expertise within and across law enforcement organisations, as well as in juxtaposition of science and practice. Highlighting this ongoing socio-technical reconfiguration of practices around the creation and presentation of digital evidence, we ask, how a legally and ethically sound implementation of AI in forensic analytics could be achieved, while processes stay feasible, usable, and efficient. With these questions, we aim to initiate a discussion of contemporary techno-solutionist visions to build “trust by design” versus the need to reconfigure practices and institutional structures to deal adequately with the challenges of digital transformation in criminal prosecution as well as in AI-supported legal services.

Session Organizers:

Dana Wilson-Kovacs, University of Exeter

David Wyatt, King's College London

Chair:

David Wyatt, King's College London

Discussant:

Matthias Wienroth, Northumbria University

215. Toxic Goodness: Harmful Legacies, Hopeful Futures – III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

How do you cultivate good practices, relationships, and things in an environment of toxicants, toxic politics, and toxic relationalities? How do toxic production systems—based on extractivism, colonialism, and plantation capitalism—foment new forms of sustainability that cannot be excised from their deadly foundations? This open call examines urgent tensions between toxic legacies and hopeful futures when it comes to so-called renewable energies, green/blue/bio-economies, waste management systems, and sustainable agriculture/aquaculture. Such hopeful alternatives to unsustainable production systems hold within them the possibility of working towards a “Greater Good,” however, “goodness” is largely built

on toxic colonial and capitalist foundations that are rendered invisible through sustainability discourse. In other words, in making sustainable things or practices, toxicities in many forms are in fact often sustained. This panel will therefore investigate the ways scientists, investors, and producers in the agricultural, aquacultural, and waste sectors build on toxic legacies as they seek to render generative material processes--such as photosynthesis, bioremediation, and fermentation--into sustainable tools. We encourage papers that empirically illuminate how social systems and material processes together shore up, generate, and maintain toxicity. Such investigations will open space to question whether and how good relations could be cultivated out of toxic relationships without assuming toxicity can be entirely expunged. The overall aim of this open panel is thus to critically address how sustainable processes depend on toxic production systems, as a first step towards activating better ways of living amid toxicity.

Participants:

Quicksilver's Tales: Alchemical Histories and Contaminated Legacies *Ruth Goldstein*

This paper examines current extractive rainforest economies in the context of alchemical histories in artisanal and small-scale gold mining (ASGM) in Peru, with a focus on the Amazonian region of Madre de Dios. As part of an ongoing collaborative research project with gold miners, indigenous communities, and environmental scientists, I bring ethnographic findings into conversation with archival materials from Incan metallurgical practices, extractive technologies and mining codes in the 16th century. Artisanal small-scale miners – (al)chemists of the rainforest – mix quicksilver with gold-flecked earth pulled from the forests subsoil and water sources. The attractive forces between the two metals creates a mercury-gold amalgam, which must be burned to leave pure gold. The blow-torch alchemy leaves quicksilver “tailings,” with small particles of gold still attached. North American and European environmental researchers and conservationists now seek methods to track and mitigate, if not eliminate the use of quicksilver in global ASGM. Chemical explanations about the disastrous health effects of mercury toxicity strikes many miners as a fabrication, a continuing legacy of colonial efforts to control the flow of natural resources. This paper's contribution to STS, particularly in Latin America, revolves around the conflict between the mistrust of miners in environmental controls and Western scientific ideas regarding chemical toxicity. I conclude with considerations of how and where (al)chemical considerations can inform environmental and economic justice, with the aim of re-writing toxic endings to quicksilver's tales.

Tracing Critical Minerals Genealogies through Arizona's Emerging Helium Boom *Kirk Jalbert, Arizona State University; J Richter, Arizona State University; Noa Bruhis, Arizona State University*

In 2018 the U.S. Department of Interior took the unprecedented step of publishing a list of minerals deemed “critical” to national security and economic development. Alongside cobalt, uranium, and lithium, helium earned a place as the only gas included on this list. Helium is one of the rarest elements on Earth, yet it is essential to many future-facing industries, including clean energy production, space exploration, energy superconductors, and microelectronics manufacturing. After decades of federal control of the helium industry, a significant private sector is now materializing with dozens of operators speculating for helium-rich gas reserves, particularly in the Western United States. Northeast Arizona is an emerging epicenter in this helium extraction boom. However, we suggest that the sociotechnical imaginaries of the helium boom are bound to prior criticality narratives imposed on the region, particularly those that precipitated the harmful legacies of uranium and coal mining. Based on two years of research, we theorize these longitudinal relationships as having critical minerals genealogies (CMGs). CMGs implicate speculative industries that utilize criticality to forward strategic interests, regulatory agencies that must navigate

criticality in forming policy, and at-risk communities making sense of criticality's implications in daily life. We contend that CMGs brings a postcolonial lens to the replications of toxic legacies in these spaces, in order to generate a dialogue of most just environmental futures.

From Mining to Phytomining: Bioinspired Practices and Hopeful Forms of Life in a Contaminated World *Lauren Kamili, EHESS/LAS/ADEME*

The former zinc mines in the village of Saint-Laurent-Le-Minier, located in the Gard region of southern France, have been closed since the 1990s. A jewel of French industry for a time, the mines and their closure have left neither the environment, whose waters and soils are now heavily polluted with zinc, lead and cadmium, nor the village, impoverished and exposed to these contaminations, unscathed. Since 2008, the Laboratory for Bio-inspired Chemistry and Ecological Innovations in Montpellier has been conducting depolluting experiments on these former mining sites using hyper-accumulating plants, which are capable of concentrating heavy metals from the soil in their roots and leaves, and are thus able to live in these toxic places. Drawing from ethnographic fieldwork both in the laboratory and in the contaminated village, this paper examines a particular project that aimed at recreating a self-sustaining ecosystem in an ecological ruin. What kind of technical, material, affective and political relationships with the plants, people and place, do these scientific bio-inspired practices produce? I first describe the technical actions that make up bio-inspiration, focusing on the system through which the vital process of plant bioaccumulation is captured and reoriented towards human projects. By partnering with plants to decontaminate this site and « grow livable worlds » (Myers 2018), chemists actually make them live in a toxic environment, forming ambivalent relationships of domestication, care and control. This regime of co-dependency and exploitation nevertheless creates the possibility for hopeful forms of life for the village, the lab, and beyond.

Residual Ecologies: Finding Life within Extraction *Sebastian Ureta, Universidad Alberto Hurtado; Patricio Flores, University of Warwick, UK*

The Carén River is a water stream located near Allhue, in central Chile. It would be completely unremarkable if it were not for one key aspect: it carries water throughout the year. Being located in a semi-arid region experiencing a decade-long megadrought, this characteristic has turned the Carén River into the source of several lively ecologies. Such availability of water has a counterintuitive source: mining waste. On the upper section of the Carén River basin lays Tranque Carén, the waste depository of Mina El Teniente, the largest subterranean mine in the world. Along with crushed rock and toxic chemical reactants, the mining waste at Carén contains a fair amount of water. Released after being treated, this water triggers the lively ecologies existing downstream from the depository. Instead of a story of toxicity, this is a story of geosymbiosis, of the intimate entanglements between water, crushed rock, chemical reactives and organic beings characterizing much of life at the Carén basin. Through geosymbioses, life at Carén emerges in the form of residual ecologies, ecologies on which human-made chemical residues occupy constitutive roles. Instead of being overtly toxic, on residual ecologies these residues are intoxicating, allowing the continuation of certain life in certain ways, but canceling out many others. Due to the current inescapability of human-made chemical pollution, residual ecologies are rapidly becoming one of the main manifestations of life on earth, an entanglement in which a plural we – humans, animals, plants and inorganic entities – must learn to live (and die) together.

Session Organizers:

Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University
Jessica Caporusso, York University
Katie Ulrich, Rice University

Chair:

Katie Ulrich, Rice University

Discussant:

Kim Fortun, University of California Irvine

216. Relations and Troubles of Tools of Valuation – VI

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

Inscribing Markets, Shaping Policy: Evaluation Devices, Socio-technical Infrastructures and the Material Semiotics of the Yield Curve *Dylan Cassar*, *University of Edinburgh*

This paper focuses on a material semiotic device sitting at the heart of fixed-income markets and central banks, known as the yield curve. Taking an Actor-Network Theory approach and drawing on 47 interviews with financial market participants and central bankers, I first argue that the yield curve as a valuation tool renders fixed-income assets commensurable and substitutable by allowing comparability and practices of 'relative value' trading. I show how, in becoming embedded in specific 'quant' evaluation cultures, the yield curve performed markets as it congealed them. Secondly, the paper argues that as central banks turned towards inflation-targeting and expectations-management as a governing mechanism, fixed-income markets became a socio-technical infrastructure for monetary policy. This infrastructure underpins the transmission mechanism of monetary policy, and therefore allows central bankers to govern via expectations as they evaluate those same expectations through the yield curve on a semiotic level. Nevertheless, I show how, as the underlying socio-technical infrastructure failed in the financial crisis of 2008, European sovereign debt crisis around 2012 and Covid crisis of 2020, central banks no longer relied purely on the semiotic element of the yield curve. As they mobilised their balance sheets in the form of Quantitative Easing, the yield curve turned into a material tool in the implementation of policy. Finally, policies like Quantitative Easing, and more recently 'Yield Curve Control', have raised questions on state 'interference' in what was previously taken as market terrain and therefore on the distortion of the yield curve as a representation of market expectations.

How Hype Begins and Ends: The Gartner Hype Cycle and Product-based Expectations *Neil Pollock*, *The University of Edinburgh*

Technological expectations or 'hype' play an important role in shaping not just the creation and adoption of technologies but also the functioning of the economy. At the centre of this shaping process are tools used by investors to decide whether to risk the early adoption of emerging technologies or wait till their prospects are more clearly established - Gartner Hype Cycles. Through drawing on interviews with Gartner analysts about how they plot technologies along a curve of over-enthusiasm and disillusionment, we explore the conditions under which hype surrounding promising technologies is judged to have begun and ended. We conceptualize the production of Hype Cycles not just as the outcome of promissory behaviour as would be done by the Sociology of Expectations but as expectation-based products. As such, we show that Gartner create and sustain the Hype Cycle through embedding it in an internal 'inventory'. We identify how this inventory creates a space for debate, how it made the reuse of components between Hype Cycles possible, but also how its use required inventive efforts to resolve specific problems created. Our analysis shows that while the beginnings/endings of hype might have multiple origins, some of these can be found in this inventory. Through revealing the importance of commodification processes for the origins of hype, our paper points to a future research agenda on product-based expectations.

Just Fines: Discounting Tables, Church Landlords, and

Reasonable Valuations, circa 1628 *William P. Deringer*, *Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)*

In the early seventeenth century, a new computational technology took hold in England: printed mathematical tables for compound interest and discounting ("present value") problems. Historians of finance and accounting have long recognized the arrival of these crucial valuation devices, predecessors of modern techniques like "discounted cash flow." Yet the early history of these tables remains hazy. What did early-seventeenth-century users do with these tables? Who used them? Why did those calculations arise when they did? This paper recovers the hidden story behind these tables, with one obscure but influential text, Ambrose Acroyd's "Tables of Leases and Interest" (1628), as guide. Two key facts emerge. First, these valuation devices were not confined to England's nascent financial sector. Rather, their foremost use related to agricultural property, specifically in assessing the "fines" tenants were required to pay landlords when leasing farms. Second, among the early adopters were institutions of the church. Anglican bishops, cathedrals, and colleges were major landowners. The unprecedented inflation of the early-modern "price revolution" had unsettled longstanding agrarian customs that had ordered the landlord-tenant relationship. Tables like Acroyd's emerged as a technical solution to a long-running conflict between church landlords and their tenants over just and reasonable fines on leases. For these users, discounting tables were not tools of instrumental rationality evident of a new capitalist mentality, but tools of social accommodation befitting an older "economy of obligation." This early-modern tale offers a vivid example of how one community first turned to a complicated mathematical algorithm in pursuit of fairness.

How auctions shape education – tendering based procurement as management tool in Swedish public education *Diana Holmqvist*, *Linköping University*

This paper aims to contribute to the open panel on governing and tools of valuation, by analysing the implicit functions of tendering based procurement as used by Swedish municipalities to organise and outsource public education to private providers. 47 procurements from 2015-2019 have been analysed. Focusing on the contract notices that set the rules of each auction and that describe what municipalities expect to buy, I show how mechanisms intended to evaluate and compare bids also have governing implications for the services that are being bought. By focusing on some key mechanisms of procurement, I argue that this is more than 'just a tool' used by human actors to outsource and organise the provision of education. By drawing on empirical examples, I show how this management tool (Chiapello & Gilbert, 2019) (1) works to commensurate complex concepts such as education into simplistic, measurable evaluation criteria used to compare tenders; (2) constructs the value of education in relation to specific conventions of worth (e.g., producing the worth of education in terms of economic value; the capacity to adapt to sudden changes; or as civic solidarity) and; (3) covertly distributes power and advantage, in accordance with the commensurations and valuations produced in every specific case. Returning to the theme of this open panel, my aim is to complicate our understanding of one ordering tool by arguing that what criteria of evaluation are set up; what conventions of worth these are based on; and how value is measured, are essential. Everything and everyone falling outside such criteria, conventions, or measurements risks being rendered unimportant, worthless, or invisible.

Organizing temporalities in a medical device market by innovation procurement *Nurgül Özbek*, *Stockholm School of Economics, Institute for Research (SIR)*; *Linus Johansson Krafve*; *Hans Kjellberg*, *Stockholm School of Economics*

This paper is about how innovation is enacted in the valuation efforts of public buyers. More particularly, it describes and analyzes how temporalities that govern innovation in a medical

device market are organized through a valuation tool and the practices related to it: procurement innovation. Valuing new technologies in markets are essentially crowded with different temporal concerns, including openness and uncertainty of the future. Innovation is inherently uncertain since its value may depend on the future developments that are yet unknown in the present. Thus, this temporal challenge in valuing ‘the real benefits’ of investments in new, high-cost medical devices often lead to tensions where the methods and practices of valuing innovation is put into question. Innovation procurement is one initiative designed to address these concerns and facilitate a ‘healthy dose’ of innovation while safeguarding better value for money in health care spending. This paper reports findings from a specific innovation procurement process of radiation therapy equipment for the New Karolinska Hospital project in Stockholm, Sweden. Based on a detailed reading of the bidding documents and interview data with the involved market actors, we identify different temporal functions of time articulated and performed by innovation procurement and how these different ways affect how innovation is enacted. Our findings serve as a basis for developing a conceptualization of organizing temporalities of medical device innovation, which contributes to STS studies of valuation tools and their part in governing economic markets.

Session Organizers:

Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech
Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna

Chair:

Kristin Asdal, TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture

217. (Dis)Trust in Public-Sector Data, Technology, and Science - I: Environment and Scientific Legitimacy

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

STS scholarship on technopolitics typically examines the role that governments and state organizations play in producing, enabling, and leveraging data, technology, and science. Technocratic projects like conducting censuses, modeling weather, producing medicines, constructing computers or developing weapons serve both state and scientific masters. While the legitimacy of these investments are often intertwined with the legitimacy of state power, such power and legitimacy also relies upon scientific development and the sustained production of technoscientific imaginaries. Yet recent years have witnessed a range of governmental actions around the world designed to purposefully delegitimize states’ technoscientific investments. Politicians work to dismantle state-funded scientific efforts, often under the guise of free-market commitments and austerity principles. The Covid-19 pandemic has revealed the global cost of distrust in public-sector science, technology, and data. Even as scientists produced a vaccine with unprecedented speed, governments around the world failed to track the spread of the virus, let alone provide data to enable decision-making. In some countries, political leaders are propagated conspiracies and “fake science”, undermining public health and scientific development. Just as governments can help advance science, technology, and data, they may also choose to strategically curb such pursuits or actively undermine their legitimacy. This panel examines how public-sector technoscientific efforts are made legitimate, and how that legitimacy is strategically undermined. We ask, how are state-sponsored science and technology projects legitimated? How can this legitimacy come undone? How can trust in public-sector technoscience be repaired? This first session focuses on environmental data and legitimacy.

Participants:

Liar, Liar, Amazon Is On Fire! Government Disinformation About Forest Fires And Distrust On Environmental Data
Kimberly Anastácio, *American University*; **Beatriz Franco**, *University of Brasilia*

Between 2019 and 2020, Brazil faced an intense fire crisis in the Amazon. The Bolsonaro administration actively tried to diminish

the crisis gravity even though public environmental data pointed out atypical numbers of fire outbreaks in rainforests. Through a qualitative content analysis of tweets published by Brazilian public authorities, we show there was a governmental attempt to misinterpret public data about Amazon fires and that this attempt was part of a broader misinformation strategy to strengthen the state’s role as the sovereign guardian of the region. We collected all tweets published by the Brazilian Environment Ministry and its minister throughout 2019 and 2020. We manually and inductively coded all posts and tried to find patterns and emergent discourses about the fire crisis. Initial findings show that the Brazilian government fostered alternative interpretations and diminished the fire data gravity to strengthen its sovereignty over a controversial and internationally targeted territory. Also, it blamed the media for focusing on fatalistic fire data in a so-called attempt to discredit the President and his team. Our early conclusion points out that governmental disinformation about the fires may not only diminish the public perception about the environmental emergency but also undermine trust in data created by public institutions themselves.

Open for Business: Data and Mutual Dependence in NOAA’s Climate Market Making *Duncan Friend, Independent Scholar*

The National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) maintains the world’s largest archive of climate data. Recently, they have worked to “catalyze” a market for climate adaptation services by promoting the use of this data to business. Such efforts include: 1) Commissioning and promoting studies of “success stories” of use of archive data by industry while soliciting suggestions for enhancements to the “data products” they use, 2) Changing their privacy policy to allow collection of more information about users and uses, and 3) Prioritizing engagement efforts by using North American Industry Classification System codes to map potential impacts and opportunities by industry sector. NOAA justifies this effort as an attempt to increase the value of their work to business and the public. However, this research finds that depending on private sector use of its data opens an avenue for business benefits to influence NOAA priorities for data collection and creation, stretching all the way to its calculation of the “Efficient Frontier” used to allocate its investments in the collection of scientific observations. This study uses participant interviews at the archive and other offices within NOAA, along with presentations and government documents to study the phenomena of mutual influence in business use of public data. It contributes to Science and Technology Studies by demonstrating how the intentional use of open data by government to accomplish its mission may create a feedback loop that brings commercial influence into decisions about the data, potentially conflicting with priorities on basic science and the public interest.

Predicting Weather with a Trustworthy AI: Analyzing Private-Public Partnership Technology Development Partnership through Sociology of Expertise *Przemyslaw Matt Lukacz, Columbia University, Department of Anthropology*

In September of 2020, the National Science Foundation (NSF)—in collaboration with other federal and private partners—announced the creation of six National Artificial Intelligence Research Institutes, which would form the backbone of a national AI strategy. One of the Institutes, the NSF AI Institute for Research on Trustworthy AI in Weather, Climate, and Coastal Oceanography (the Institute) is dedicated to the advancement of the NSF’s agenda for use-inspired, trustworthy AI and to forging collaborations between academia, industry, and the private sector. I use documentary analysis and interviews to understand how a team of experts in AI, earth sciences, and risk assessment who were behind the Institute’s formation instigated a vision of the future of environmental forecasting such that it fits into a national imaginary. This paper questions how public-sector

technoscientific efforts are legitimized. To this end, I mobilize the literature on the sociology of expertise to 1), show how the formation of “alternative expertise networks” (Eyal, 2013) lead intermediary professional positions and spaces to emerge, and 2), ask what role “trustworthy AI” as a boundary object plays in this process. More specifically, I show how “alternative expertise networks” shape, and are shaped by, visions of “civic science” (Fortun, 2004) and “scientific imaginaries” (Jasanoff & Kim, 2016). In effect, the Institute is positioned as a mediating organization to increase trust in the use of AI in environmental science among weather forecasters and the public, but also to forge a closer partnership between the data analytics industry and federal science.

Social trust in science-based decision-making in a contested environmental context *Valerie Berseht, Department of Sociology, University of British Columbia; Ralph Mathews, Department of Sociology, University of British Columbia*

Despite efforts to increase public engagement in fisheries governance, the legitimacy of science-based management continues to be challenged by a wide range of non-state actors. This paper investigates social trust in government efforts to mobilize scientific knowledge related to salmon management in British Columbia, Canada. Salmon management is a substantial technoscientific project upheld by state apparatuses that employ scientific methods to gather and feed evidence into decision-making. We present data from 137 interviews with representatives from federal government, non-governmental organizations, recreational and commercial fishing, and Nuu-chah-nulth First Nations. We compare the “trust repertoires” (Mizrachi et al., 2007) through which these diverse groups assess the legitimacy of state efforts to manage salmon fisheries along four dimensions: trust in data, trust in individuals, trust in government, and trust in process. We find that even where there is trust in scientific knowledge generally, histories of natural resource conflict and perceptions of politically motivated decision-making undermine confidence in the state’s ability to sustainably manage fisheries. Moreover, public trust in decision-making is affected by broader contextual factors including scientific uncertainty, conditions of resource scarcity, and ecological complexity. Localized governance structures which feature long term, sustained co-management have been successful in building trust through good relations. However, respondents identify deeper changes needed to improve the legitimacy of knowledge mobilization at other levels of governance. These findings contribute a multi-dimensional analysis of social trust to STS scholarship on technopolitics and the politics of knowledge production.

Recoding Scientific Legitimacy *Cindy Kaiying Lin, University of Michigan; Cornell University*

The planet is aflame. Historians call it the Pyrocene, a Fire Age comparable to the Ice Ages, threatening lives across the world. In Indonesia, an epicenter of this moment, global fire detection sensors installed by American federal agencies are key for fire prevention over the last three decades. With rising rates of undetected peatland fires, Indonesian politicians have slowed partnerships with federal agencies and employed IBM to develop fire prediction technologies. This paper takes its focus the redesign of global fire detection sensors, from the late 1990s and beyond, as they come to symbolize the displacement of government science agencies by major tech corporations. Global as they may seem, fire detection sensors are continually updated to capture the specificities of fire regimes. The resulting sensors then integrate fire prevention with local narratives of the key perpetrators of fires. In late 1990s Indonesia, global fire detection sensors showed evidence of agribusinesses clearing peatland illegally. Based on 18 months of ethnographic fieldwork in Jakarta, this paper shows how, two decades later, fire detection technologies are redesigned to criminalize a new actor. In the early 2010s, Indonesian politicians attributed undetected fires to

small farmers burning plots of land which cannot be seen by fire sensors. These sensors, at first, came to symbolize the failure of American science. Now, they are redesigned by major tech corporations to criminalize small farmers. This paper considers how public sector technologies today are sites to reconfigure who can produce legitimate scientific data and its role in political affairs.

Habeas Habermas : How Does The Digital Circulation Of Information Shape Legitimacy In The Public Sphere? *Anne L. Washington, New York University; Kandrea Wade, CU Boulder*

Habeas corpus, a Latin legal term, demands that governments legitimate their authority. The move towards digital government unleashed new debates over authority and legitimacy. A decade ago, the technopolitics of open data promised rational decision-making through data exchange. Unlike the distribution of information through coffee houses in the public sphere imagined by Habermas (1990), more data provided less certainty and fewer informed debates. Competing interests no longer rely on the same evidence to legitimate their position. Contemporary publics evolve around relationships with what Mark Warner (2002) calls an “addressable object” that centers reality and bounds unrelated individuals. Originally limited to the circulation of print journalism, a public or counter-public (Fraser, 1990) may emerge around the distribution of a text broadly construed to include videos, images, or even spreadsheets. Evelyn Ruppert (2013) studied datasets that center discursive conversations that often challenge the state in what she calls “data publics”. How does the digital circulation of information shape the legitimacy of data publics, counterpublics, and the state? We consider two examples that demonstrate these dynamics. In early-stage research, we interrogate counter publics emerging within marginalized communities around the circulation of digital material in response to the state. A longitudinal ethnography illustrates how financial open data, generated through digital regulatory compliance, simultaneously built legitimacy through policy and undermined it through implementation. We reflect on who has the authority to confer the legitimacy of data and how this engages with the technopolitics of state power.

Session Organizers:

danah boyd, Microsoft Research / Data & Society
Janet Vertesi, Princeton University

Chair:

Alondra Nelson, Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton

218. Building ties across countries: Scientific collaboration and mobility in global scientific relationships

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Forging Better Global Partnerships: Towards a New Transnational Feminist Research Paradigm *Jessica Lee Mathiason, University of Maryland*

Transnational feminist STS scholars including Subramaniam, Hamilton, and Willey have critiqued multi-national genomic research initiatives (“co-creations”) between developing and developed countries for their uncritical reification of colonial legacies, use of diasporic proxies, and treatment of the Global South as a “living laboratory.” Using the ongoing H3Africa collaboration as a paradigmatic example, I extend research on how existing practices and methods exacerbate “unequal and uncertain worlds” before proposing an alternative paradigm. First, I interrogate how a research enterprise aimed not at creating a diverse map of haplotypes for Western researchers but at “building capacity” in Africa, practices covert medical imperialism under the guise of health justice. Second, informed by Dickenson’s critique of pharmacogenetics, I argue that by

assuming racialized, genetic similarity among all Africans and focusing on the role single genes play in complex conditions like kidney disease, H3Africa reinforces an individualistic model of disease causation and treatment. This shifts resources away from public health improvements like antiretrovirals and living-donor transplant facilities and towards genetic screening, personal responsibility, and targeted drug therapies with limited efficacy. Finally, I draw on Black feminist epistemologies pioneered by Bailey and Peoples to propose a transnational research framework that: (a) allows research questions to emerge from the daily needs of African citizens; (b) conceives of health as environmental and collective instead of enclosed within the individual body; (c) generates data that is open-source rather than proprietary; (d) maximizes public health, putting the well-being of living citizens over the potential future benefit of those not-yet-born.

Gender and Global Scholarly Authorship Networks: a Cross-country, Cross-Disciplinary Analysis *Kjersten Bunker Whittington, Reed College; Molly King, Santa Clara University; Isabella Cingolani, Elsevier*

Global and team science approaches are on the rise, as is attention to the network underpinnings of gender disparities in scientific productivity. Many network studies of men's and women's collaboration rely on bounded case studies of single disciplines and/or countries, and often rely on limited measures related to the collaborative process. Our rich data source of over 1.2 million authors and 144 million collaborative relationships allows for an exceptionally detailed capture of (global and unbounded) scientific co-authorship networks that span national boundaries and include intra- and interdisciplinary co-authorship ties across time. We focus on researchers in four academic knowledge subjects (Biochemistry, Business and Economics, Engineering, and Medicine) and four geographic locations (United States, Brazil, Europe (EU 28) and Japan) and include data on their connections that reach beyond these boundaries. We pay particular attention to how connected authors are (degree centrality), attributes of authors' collaborative relationships, the "quality" and other characteristics of these ties, tendencies towards gender homophily, and the nature of men's and women's interdisciplinary and international reach. We find that men tend to have more advantageous first-order connections, yet the second-order collaborative profiles of men and women look more similar. Men and women exhibit significant preferential attachment to authors of the same gender, and this is consistent over time. We discuss country-, discipline-, and cohort-specific variation - in particular, findings of greater gender gaps among scientists in so-called gender "progressive" countries and disciplines - and situate our findings for STS literature on the global landscape of science production.

The global network of air links and scientific collaboration – a quasi-experimental analysis *Adam Ploszaj, University of Warsaw; Xiaoran Yan, Indiana University Bloomington; Katy Börner, Indiana University Bloomington*

We study the impact of long-haul flights availability/introduction on international scientific collaboration. The main advantage of our project is the use of a quasi-experimental approach. Specifically, we employ a discontinuity in the global air links network that results from regulatory requirements, as identified by Campante & Yanagizawa-Drott (2017). Their analysis shows that cities that are just under 6,000 miles apart are distinctly more likely to have direct air links, compared with cities slightly above that threshold. This discontinuity—arguably exogenous—allowed them to use a quasi-experimental framework to analyze the causal relationship between air flights and economic development (using night lights satellite data) and business links (international firm ownership data). Our analysis uses a similar analytical framework to international scientific collaboration measured by co-authorships of scientific articles and patents, co-

affiliations, and citations. For this purpose, we use geocoded affiliations of publications and patents from Microsoft Academic Graph (MAG) and publications from Web of Science (WOS), as well as flight data available from International Civil Aviation Organization. Our analysis covers the period from 1989 to 2017 and uses regression discontinuity design and instrumental variable identification strategies.

Turkey's Integration to Research Networks and Research Networks' Effects on Scientific Studies: The Case of METU *Arsev Umur Aydinoglu, Middle East Technical University; Ayse Isilak, Middle East Technical University Science and Technology Policy Studies*

The literature on research and development (R&D), economic development and policy design suggest that understanding dynamics of research processes, i.e. "science of science" is crucial in shaping efficient policies. As Wagner has indicated, "modern science is intensely social" and collaboration is good a way to provide necessary resources including physical capital, knowledge, and capabilities. In line with that, increasing role of research networks and globalization of science are among the recent tendencies in the science of science. Countries are also promoting "internationalization" of their scientific systems. As such, this study aims to answer how Turkey's integration with research networks should be structured considering Turkey's recent targets related to scientific productivity. In this respect, using mixed methods approach—combination of bibliometric assessment and interviews—we provide an overview of Turkey's integration to research networks, factors affecting network choices, and an evaluation of the effects of networks on research in the case of Middle East Technical University (METU). Preliminary findings indicate that educational background of researchers and attendance to international conferences are important channels for networks access; infrastructure, capabilities of the partners and funding channels are critical factors for network preferences. Furthermore, improvements can be made on a wide range of issues including funding, recruitment, promotion, and staff policies of the universities.

Session Organizer:

Zaida Chinchilla-Rodríguez, Consejo Superior Investigaciones Científicas (CSIC), Instituto de Políticas y Bienes Públicos (IPP)

219. Choosing to Refuse, Repair, or Rend Asunder in Technological Practice

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Recent work in tech industry activism sees promise in organizing efforts like "#TechWontBuildIt" as tech employees refuse to work in protest of their employers' contracts with the U.S. Immigration and Customs Enforcement. These efforts highlight a need for more thorough discussions around the category of 'tech work' and the obligation not to design (Baumer, 2011). STS scholars have long critiqued the notion that all problems can be fixed with technology, and emphasized that technology is not an inherent good in itself. These critiques of technological solutionism prove all the more challenging when the question is not whether to implement a new device or system, but whether and how existing systems merit repair and revitalization, for what reasons and by what means. When infrastructures become taken for granted even as they permeate daily life (Star, 1999); it often feels like repair is the only option when these systems break down (Jackson, 2014). This should lead to critical interrogation: Who calls for repair? Who undertakes it? Who benefits from the maintenance of a system, and who remains subjugated by its continuance? In other words, we need to create a technology design culture that can recognize when and to whom a technology will be harmful, as well as able to refuse and dismantle harmful technology.

Participants:

Tech Worker Oral Histories of Resistance and Refusal *Sarah*

Myers West, Annenberg School for Communication & Journalism, University of Southern California

Tech firms today are permeated by networks of workers organizing for change: in the past several years, we have seen protests over military and law enforcement deployments of invasive surveillance tools, workplace discrimination, and tech's climate impact. As tech worker organizing receives increased public attention - and begins to formalize through associations with unions - it can also be traced as a legacy of a long tradition of tech resistance both inside and outside the confines of Silicon Valley. Groups like Computer People for Peace, Computer Professionals for Social Responsibility and the Polaroid Revolutionary Workers Movement, among others, are part of this history. Putting today's waves of worker organizing in dialogue with the past, I discuss the early findings of an oral history project that examines collective memories of tech resistance. In particular, I focus on factors that shape notions of solidarity and the formation of movements among tech workers across different positionalities including issue area, work status, race, gender, class, and nationality - what leads workers to join together across the structural and company-designed barriers keeping them apart? In asking these questions, this project adds to a growing body of research, particularly within science and technology studies, exploring questions that tie together technology and labor, interrogate tech companies as powerful political actors, and consider how working conditions shape the development and deployment of technologies - and how they might be changed.

Mobilizing to Refuse: Organizing for Tech Abolition *Britt Paris, Rutgers University, School of Communication and Information*

Both currently and historically, the concept of abolition is used to characterize practices that seek to end, not reform, social systems that disproportionately harm portions of the population. I illustrate how abolition work has been built up in response to technocratic overreach of police forces, and how this is distinct from data efforts around police reform as they have grown and changed over the last six years. The reform efforts assume that police can be reformed with enough data. But there is never enough data. Data reform efforts are meaningless if they are not motivated by political will. Through this set of projects, we see that data, as well as calls for technocratic intervention in a number of areas in the name of reform can be a barrier to doing things, a pressure valve to ensure nothing meaningful changes. To push for more normative discussions around power and oppression in technological research, development, and deployment, I offer a concept of abolition that can be used as tool to "organize ourselves", within academic technical research communities to better attend to privilege and power in situations of participatory or sociotechnical design; think critically about how we relate to one another and the systems we design and deploy; the demands we make of communities of non-designers; and offer guidelines, questions, and ideas to think about to mobilize practitioners to build new practices to refuse and dismantle the harms produced by technology design and deployment.

Hacker, Piecemaker, Labor Organizer? Commodification and Resistance in the Bug Bounty Industry *Yuan Stevens, Ryerson University*

Crowdsourced vulnerability disclosure, at once a form of outsourced quality assurance and rewards-based competition, is now a common practice in hacking communities. In the wake of the 2008 recession, multiple startups have emerged (e.g. HackerOne, Bugcrowd) that market themselves as "bug bounty" platforms. This paper renders visible the objects of transaction in this robust and growing industry: bug bounty platforms are temporary work agencies that commodify the labor of hackers as piecemeal workers, selling their services to institutions wishing to draw on the wisdom of the hacker crowd. Hackers in the bug

bounty industry, like other global gig workers, generally lack adequate labor protections. Bug bounty platforms provide bug bounty programs as a service and are additive for many companies' security postures, with the result that the workers doing this labor are also rendered additive and treated as expendable. Drawing on a multi-year interdisciplinary project involving interviews with 40 hackers and hacker experts, and based in part on a forthcoming research report co-authored with Ryan Ellis for Data & Society Research Institute, this paper also examines how bug bounty workers in the US, Europe, and India (comprising a large portion of the workforce) have used various technical and organizing tactics for resistance as they undertake this critical repair work.

Refusing to Start: How the automotive aftermarket decides to repair, develop, or walk away *MC Forelle, Cornell University*

When automotive hobbyists and aftermarket entrepreneurs invest in a car, they think about more than just fixed costs like purchase price and loan payments; they also consider the availability of parts, of schematics for constructing their own parts, or of the very materials for building those parts. These concerns apply beyond material components - increasingly, independent repair, modification, and aftermarket parts development projects require access to a car's software and the data it produces. Original equipment manufacturers often make this work difficult, blocking the access to the necessary computer programs or parts designs that interoperators need. What's more, the rapid development of new product versions (plus their planned obsolescence) can make sourcing necessary parts, or even the materials with which to build to parts, difficult or impossible. This project combines industry analysis with fieldwork with car hobbyists and automotive aftermarket product manufacturers to explore how they decide to work with, or refuse to work with, some car models over others. What emerges is a complicated network of supply chains, digital infrastructures, and cultural iconographies that reflect troubling power dynamics between manufacturers and downstream consumers, with serious implications for environmental sustainability, data justice, and digital ownership.

Session Organizers:

MC Forelle, Cornell University

Sarah Myers West, Annenberg School for Communication & Journalism, University of Southern California

220. Algorithmic Governance in Unequal and Uncertain Contexts

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

This panel interrogates the functions and effects of algorithms in contemporary governance. It seeks to conceptualize the notion of context in algorithmic governance by, first, perceiving algorithmic governance as an activity taking place in a variety of unequal and uncertain contexts, and aiming at investigating these contexts in a systematic manner. Second, by focusing not only on how algorithms are used as tools for governance, but also on how such tools can be governed - controlled and held to account - and what challenges such forms of governance imply. The use of algorithms in society can imply a moving of contestable issues from negotiable to non-negotiable spaces, thereby reducing agency of human actors. Active recontextualizations can become an important tool to problematize such and other consequences of algorithmic governance and reveal possible unintended implications and effects (such as inequality and injustice). The papers contribute to STS debates on two key themes. First, multiplying the contexts of algorithmic governance and discussing how specific conditions impact upon the efficacy and perceived legitimacy of algorithms as tools for governance. This includes the manifold everyday practices through which algorithmic governance is effectuated as well as the legal, political, cultural, economic, and technological frames that predispose and tacitly guide these. The second focuses on the fact that algorithms are themselves governed by human and non-human agents. The increased use of algorithms in all areas of life makes the question of how to

understand and control such governing algorithms a timely and salient area of inquiry.

Participants:

What is Algorithmic Governance? *Shiv Issar, University of Wisconsin - Milwaukee; A. Aneesh, University Of Wisconsin, Milwaukee*

The notion of algorithmic governance and the term, algorithm have gained sufficient traction in the social sciences to raise certain difficulties. Paul Dourish (2016) in particular, has methodically challenged the proliferation of non-computer science literature on algorithms and algorithmic governance. In computer science, algorithms and their various types are clearly defined as abstract, formalized descriptions of computational procedures. From that perspective, it is confusing that algorithms are variously interpreted as code, program, automation, or architecture in the humanities and social sciences. Seeking to resolve conflicting understandings of algorithmic governance, this paper traces its history to the broad architecture of the universal Turing Machine and its systemic logic in terms of algocracy. As no governance is possible by algorithms alone, algorithmic governance is analyzed as a type of governance assemblage where various elements come together to produce automatic, machinic, and programmed governance. With its tendency to execute pre-programmed outcomes, the rise of algorithmic governance becomes a matter of concern in cases where it reduces social negotiability, which is central to philosophical justifications for democracy. We identify a common thread of critical concern regarding algorithmic governance: actual and possible institutional action to move contestable issues to a space of reduced negotiability. Three clearly defined domains of concern are highlighted: the problem of arbitrary power (surveillance), arbitrary discrimination (social bias), and arbitrary identification (system identity).

Never send a human to do a machine's job? A cross-platform analysis of policies, mechanisms, and practices of automated agent governance *Mykola Makhortykh, University of Bern; Felix Victor Münch, Leibniz Institute for Media Research | Hans Bredow Institute (HBI); Aleksandra Urman, University of Bern; Amélie Heldt, Leibniz Institute for Media Research | Hans Bredow Institute (HBI); Stephan Dreyer, Leibniz Institute for Media Research | Hans Bredow Institute (HBI); Matthias C. Kettemann, Leibniz Institute for Media Research | Hans Bredow Institute (HBI)*

The continuous growth of online platforms is accompanied by the increasing use of automation for providing and utilizing their services. One form of automation, which is increasingly (ab)used by platform users for a multitude of tasks (e.g., content distribution and moderation, but also opinion manipulation and vandalism), are automated agents or bots. To understand how technical (e.g., velocity) and normative (e.g., the accountability of users for the actions of agents they deploy) aspects of agent use are regulated by different types of platforms (e.g., social media or messengers), we conduct a cross-platform analysis of automated agent governance. Using document analysis, we look at three different forms of governance: 1) platform-wide policies; 2) developer-centered mechanisms; 3) and user- and developer-made practices. Our findings highlight different governance paradigms (e.g., “Wild West” and “risk assessment”) as well as general tendency to overpolice the agents via non-transparent mechanisms.

Reddit à la Russe: how socio-technical alliances in user-driven media cultivate critical publics in Russia *Olga Dovbysh, University of Helsinki*

The role of humans is among the core elements of the current academic debate concerning the non-neutrality of algorithms, i.e. the understanding that algorithmic systems cannot move beyond the agency that has been programmed into them (Klinger &

Svensson 2018). This paper situates itself within the scholarship investigating those who design, develop, operate, and manage algorithmic systems. While much scholarly work, including studies of news and social media, examines these socio-technical alliances of human and non-human actors in democratic contexts, this paper tests current theoretical assumptions by looking at Russia. It draws upon in-depth interviews with journalists, editors and IT professionals involved in two Russian user-driven media platforms: Pikabu and TJournal. Both are notable for their high level of automation, including elaborate ranking, recommendation and sorting algorithms. They also have a reputation for fostering a free atmosphere, within which users can publish and discuss social and political issues.

Artistic Responses to Algorithmic Governance: Reimagining and Transgressing Algorithmic Imaginaries *Holger Pötzsch, UiT - The Arctic University of Norway; Gabriel Pereira, Aarhus University*

This paper investigates artistic responses to algorithmic governance. Based on the theoretical frameworks of Cornelius Castoriadis and Jacques Rancière, we devise a terminology to describe how artworks and practices engage with received systems of automated data capture, analysis, and operationalisation. Focusing on techniques of defamiliarization and transgression, we develop a heuristic typology of tactics available to artists to question algorithmic systems, including: appropriating, rejecting, inverting (perspectives, scales, values/norms), and creating alternatives. These tactics are used to challenge, subvert, and ultimately reimagine dominant algorithmic technologies and the specific frames of sensing, speaking, and doing they imply. In a generative inquiry, we develop categories through engagements with a series of relevant cultural expressions and systematize our findings in a table that shows our evolving classification. Through our inquiry, we hope to contribute to the mapping of a somewhat muddled field thereby facilitating further attempts to creatively reimagine and actively reshape contemporary societies in a more inclusive and just manner.

Session Organizer:

Gabriel Pereira, Aarhus University

221. Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy/Session 4: Pandemic Publics

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

The Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy (CompCoRe) project, comprising over sixty scholars with interdisciplinary expertise in STS, law, public policy, and the social sciences, has spent a year analyzing national policy responses to the pandemic in sixteen countries across five continents (website: compcore.cornell.edu). Our analysis shows that the pandemic is not simply a public health crisis to be managed by listening to “science” as conventional wisdom would have it. Rather, the Covid-19 crisis is playing out in unexpected and non-linear ways within the interlocking arenas of public health, economy, and politics against a continually shifting terrain of scientific, socioeconomic, and political developments. Our research identifies patterned responses across countries that demonstrate how the pandemic found and exacerbated underlying structural weaknesses in national response systems, and it highlights the need for reforms in current institutional approaches to preparedness in global health crises. Countries represented in CompCoRe include Australia, Austria, Brazil, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, Peru, Singapore, South Korea, Sweden, Taiwan, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The panel will feature comparative analyses of national efforts to enroll reliable epidemiological and biomedical expertise, resolve difficult trade-offs, manage the economic fallout of the pandemic, and build political support for effective implementation, among other topics. We aim to open up new questions about public health sovereignty, crisis management, and global flows of knowledge and power among experts, states, and citizens. You can learn more about CompCoRe at compcore.cornell.edu.

Participants:

Between Response-able Citizens and Simple Policy Objects:

Making pandemic Publics in Parliamentary Discourse and Legal Intervention in Austria. *Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies; Iris Eisenberger, University of Graz*

This paper investigates the dynamic and performative construction of pandemic publics in Austria, with a specific focus on two arenas: parliamentary discourses and different legal interventions such as statutory acts and administrative regulations. We thus will explore both as arenas in which fragmented perceptions, values and practices get assembled in more or less coherent manners, and where the tensions between matters of facts and matters of concern become visible. This allows us to observe the non-coherent and multiple performances of pandemic publics. They linger between the “response-able citizen” as a necessary political fiction and the citizen as a “policy object” to be regulated to assure compliance to the pandemic situation. The former notion refers to the explicitly expressed ideal that the performance of pandemic facts will quasi-automatically lead reasonable citizens to “right” actions, behaviors and compliances. The notion of “policy objects”, however, refers to the tacit construction of citizens who need clear legal orders with corresponding consequences for transgressions. We will reflect how over the past year political actors have navigated between these two conceptualisations of citizens and the related modes of governance in the Austrian context.

Inequalities and the Imagined Public: Cohesive and Fractured Assumptions within the UK's Scientific Advice. *Rokia Ballo, University College London; Warren Pearce, iHuman/Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield; Jack Stilgoe, University College London; James Wilsdon, University of Sheffield*

By the start of 2021, the UK was in the midst of a disastrous second wave of deaths from Covid-19, and had the highest per capita death rate of any large country. Yet the UK had previously been identified as one of the countries best prepared for any future pandemic. This gap between preparedness and performance continues to demand explanation. In this paper, we contribute to this effort by revealing the “imagined public” within the UK's scientific advice. This imagined public constitutes a key set of framing assumptions that help to make sense of the country's broader pandemic response. Our paper aims to make these assumptions explicit, and show how the imagined public went through cycles of cohesion and fracture in the fraught months of February-June 2020. Analysing official minutes and press briefings, we identify three characteristics of the imagined public: (1) a ‘freedom-loving’ public resistant to stringent policy interventions; (2) the public as part of a societal ‘machine’, subject to precision control from the centre in order to achieve policy goals; (3) a public that was, in an echo of wartime rhetoric, ‘all in it together’. We focus particularly on the tensions between a singular imagined public and the multiple health inequalities that became increasingly stark as the pandemic developed. We conclude by considering the implications of our analysis, both for understanding the UK's response to Covid and for the future practice of scientific advice.

The Pandemic in the Changing Social Compact: Challenges of the Japanese Case. *Kyoko Sato, Stanford University; Kohta Juraku, Tokyo Denki University; Mikihiro Tanaka, Waseda University*

The pandemic revealed the underlying structural inequality and unfairness in Japan as it did elsewhere. Notably, it also highlighted and intensified distinct features of newly emerging political culture in which the trust in the central government has diminished even further and the public has become more

politically polarized and fragmented, as well as the challenges of risk/crisis communication in such a context. Even though cumulative confirmed numbers of cases and deaths remained lower than many other countries, the government's approaches were criticized for lacking in consistency, principles, or long-term strategies. Experts also received opposing critiques from the left (“too lenient” “compromised by interests”) and the right (“too restrictive” “killing the economy”), making effective communication difficult. In particular, restrictive, targeted use of PCR tests and the pessimistic prediction presented by a governmental advisor based on theoretical epidemiology in earlier months became a highly contentious domain where conflicting views remain unresolved still today, even after tests became widely available. Furthermore, when earlier approaches that relied mostly on voluntary behavioral guidelines became ineffective and legally binding restrictions were introduced, this incited polarized reactions. These tensions show divergent responses to changing relationships among individual citizens, their communities, and the state that Japan has been going through in the face of a long economic decline and the erosion of national identity as a strong world power. The paper will examine the challenges of expert advising and science communication in this political context of Japan, and explore potential remedies.

Sweden's Pandemic Response *Tobias Olofsson, Lund University*

Closing Remarks: Making a New Social Compact for the Next Pandemic. *Stephen Hilgartner, Department of Science & Technology Studies/ Cornell University*

Session Organizers:

Sheila Jasanoff, Harvard University

Stephen Hilgartner, Department of Science & Technology Studies/ Cornell University

Ben Hurlbut, Arizona State University

Onur Ozgode, Harvard STS Program, Harvard Kennedy School

Margarita Rayzberg, Cornell University STS

222. Decolonizing the Canon - Part I

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Participants:

“I Can Only Conclude What They Feel By the State of Their Institutions”: James Baldwin and Questioning Canons as Technologies of White Supremacy *Lisa Ann Avron, Cornell University*

This talk hopes to open a conversation about the very concept of a canon, inquiring what these technologies for institution building are meant to do and what they are meant to preserve. More specifically, I want to speak through James Baldwin's famous public lecture, wherein he denounces the liberal sentimental definition of racism—a “feeling” of hatred—and instead directs our attention to the material institutions built to maintain white political, economic, and cultural supremacy, stating that, while he may not know whether any particular white person “hates” him, he can draw conclusions based on the evidence of anti-black inequality apparent in “the state of their institutions.” So then, what is the state of the STS institution, as read through an analysis of its canon? And are essential(ist) STS canons helping us build-up our discourses and/or holding us back from growth and from our ability to, in bell hooks' (1994) words, “teach to transgress” white supremacy? Please come prepared for a discussion.

Not Another Controversy: Making Theory Matter in STS *SY Cheung*

Is this “STS enough?” This paper is a provocation for dismantling the boundaries between “mainstream” STS and its more critical strands of inquiry, including feminist, postcolonial and critical race STS. Public interest in STS has accelerated as

events such as climate change, racial capitalism, rising illiberalism, and of course pandemics, among others, call for new ways of understanding how technoscience is implicated in creating our current world of compounding crises. Yet, internal debates on whether "STS proper" should engage in and intervene upon such issues persist. Alarming, some scholars are reluctant to associate with STS because they disagree with the politics and limitations of theories such as symmetry, constructivism and actor-network theory which developed during the field's early growth stage. This paper charts the new theoretical contours of an emerging critical turn in STS. It asks why these approaches are not considered "mainstream" when they are vital for creating STS theories that matter to social policy, public discourse and justice. It invites scholars to place power at the center of STS thought and attend to how the institutions and practices of science, technology and medicine facilitate our current crisis of unequal accumulation.

Reclaiming my kin in STS: Ethnographic refusal of the Western knowledge canon *Tiên-Dung Hà, Stanford University*

How can we decenter or decolonize the Western centric canon of STS without centering on, and in turn, reinforcing its own colonial forces? And more broadly, has colonialism really finished? The paper seeks to challenge the assumptions that colonialism is an artifact of the past and we should only be concerned with the afterlife of colonialism (Stoler, 2013) in the production of knowledge, especially in the global South. In this paper, I will reclaim my own kin in STS by attending to Audra Simpson's practice of "ethnographic refusal." In Mohawk Interruptus (2014), Simpson demonstrates that to obtain real political recognition is to refuse the reproduction of the Western canon of knowledge, to question the authority and legitimacy of those in power, and to challenge the basic notions of citizenship and membership that can perpetuate while occluding the violent histories of settler colonialism. Simpson's "ethnographic refusal" not only captures the power in the Mohawk's refusal to accept Canadian citizenship, but also questions the representation of knowledge that keeps reinforcing Western domination. I argue that "ethnographic refusal" is an important and useful method and practice for STS scholars to unsettle the Western paradigm STS and critically examine its entanglements with ongoing colonial forces that shape scientific knowledge production in the global South.

Resisting Eurocentrism in STS and Area Studies *Elise K Burton, University of Toronto*

This paper is the personal reflection of an early career scholar trained in Middle East area studies and subsequently hired into an STS faculty position. Both area studies and STS are regularly described as interdisciplinary fields of research, open to a wide range of topics, methodologies, and theoretical approaches. Clearly defined canons of scholarship, to the point of requisite citation practices in syllabi and publications, would appear to be antithetical to such a commitment to interdisciplinarity. However, patterns of exclusion have circumscribed my own experience in both STS and area studies, revealing unexpected boundaries to the topics considered legible or generative by either field. Despite abundant self-critique within both fields, STS and area studies remain substantially driven by their institutional and intellectual roots as research of "policy-relevant" topics for Europe and its settler-colonies. Can a scholar of science in Middle Eastern societies overcome the Eurocentric constraints of area studies, which imagines science in the "non-West" or "Global South" to be a product of interactions with the "West" alone? Perhaps more pertinent, can STS incorporate theory and methods from other parts of the world through anything other than an area studies framework? In the context of teaching majority non-white students, of what use are STS theories premised upon presumed-white subjects with unfettered access to material resources and the newest technologies? I explore these questions through reflections on publishing and on

teaching undergraduate courses, seeking paths toward productive and meaningful inclusion of more people and places in STS.

Session Organizer:

Tiên-Dung Hà, Stanford University

Discussant:

Max Liboiron, Memorial University of Newfoundland and Labrador

223. Radical Care in Feminist Digital Spaces I

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

The increasing digitalization of everyday life reveals a growing activity/presence of feminist practices in the digital sphere (D'Ignazio and Klein 2020; Jarvis 2009; McLean 2020). Such practices reconfigure the digital space and generate more safe, just, inclusive and unoppressive places (Young 1986) that challenge sexist and exclusionary practices. Moreover, in the recent/ongoing pandemic crisis where the digital sphere has augmented, (digital) care practices have gained a distinctive and leading role in people's everyday lives. Standing against the neoliberal tradition of individualism and commodification, 'radical care is often connected to positive political change by providing spaces of hope in dark times' (Hobart and Kneese, 2020: x). In a world overwhelmed by systemic sexism and multiple crises of care, crises of care, such emancipatory possibilities of digital space are bound to play a central role. This panel shifts attention towards feminist practices of radical care in the digital space and explores their genealogies, characteristics, dynamics, and limitations. We welcome contributions using transdisciplinary and intersectional methods to discuss digital care as related with understandings of inclusion, solidarity and interdependence. How can we theorize a more expanded notion, language and practice of care in the digital space? What would an understanding of radical care mean in relation with data management, digital security and infrastructure? How can radical practices challenge institutional carelessness and 'carewashing'? How are existing platforms (re)shaped in more inclusive ways through intersectional practices of care? How does an STS perspective trouble notions of radical care, feminism and digital space? How can STS research on radical care and feminist digital practices reinforce and promote feminist knowledge production?

Participants:

Care/harm in digital spaces: A feminist reading *Jessica McLean, Macquarie University; Sophia Maalsen, The University of Sydney*

Digital storytelling has emerged as a ubiquitous way to communicate care, and sometimes enact harm, at multiple scales during COVID-19. Digital technologies are allowing people to share narratives and experiences that captures how they adapt, recover and resist the damaging aspects of health and economic crises via digital technologies. We focus on care to appreciate the diverse ways that humans and more-than-humans are co-producing digital geographies while facilitating narratives that maintain and repair our worlds so we can live as well as possible. But harm is also facilitated by digital storytelling and considering how the same technologies facilitate opposite processes makes for challenging digital spaces. A feminist digital geographic approach helps to read the effects of these changes as it uses an integrated lens on spatial and justice issues. As the boundaries between public and private places have blurred with spatial and physical distancing and produced changed worlds, digital devices are mediating, enabling and constraining forms of care and harm with a new intensity.

More Heavy Processing: Exploring Feminist Digital Archival Practice *Jessica M. Lapp, University of Toronto*

Feminist archiving projects are concerned with addressing partial accounts, historical amnesia, and under-documented moments, people, and events. Increasingly, digital collections and community-operated archival platforms are providing access to feminist records and histories outside of more formal institutional repositories. This paper employs the concept of 'heavy

processing' to explore how feminist organizers are creating and circulating digital records and collections. Elaborating on Caswell and Cifor's (2016) call for archivists to enact radical empathy through a feminist ethics of care, and Cowan and Rault's (2020) writing on the digital recordkeeping practices of trans feminist and queer communities, this paper explores the creation and circulation of feminist records through examples from Rise Up! A Digital Feminist Archive, Alternative Toronto, and the Sallie Bingham Center for Women's History and Culture. In reflecting on interviews with record creators, archivists, and archival users I argue that the documentation and representation of feminist and queer lives needs to be heavy with expectation, responsibility, care, and obligation. A call for more heavy processing directs our gaze towards the long term, and often slow, processes that enable careful approaches to information circulation, attribution, access and use. This work contributes to the field of feminist STS by positioning digital archives as systems of feminist knowledge production and circulation that are shaped and re-shaped through practices of care and mutual responsibility.

Third Space Walks. A Mobile Method In Virtual And Material Spaces Of Cities. *Mirjana Mitrovic, Universität der Künste Berlin*

The interaction between technologies and societies shape everyday life in urban spaces as the boundaries between virtual and analog worlds seem to dissolve. Concepts like "hybridity" applied by Haraway and "Third Space" according to Bhabha create a possibility to understand, influence and debate current and future dynamics of digitalization. To walk this new space, this paper presents a new method of flânerie, based on Benjamin and established theories of walking, such as psychogeography or strolology, but including feminist, intersectional and postcolonial perspectives. It understands flânerie not only as walking, but also as collecting impressions from different perspectives and presenting – perhaps fragmented – conclusions. Applied by various persons whom are not included in the prevalent image of the flâneur as a white man, this method challenges the status quo of how and by whom academic knowledge is created and represented. Through this method and a focus on the trinity of digital technologies, bodies and spaces, the third space and what it means to those who walk it can be analyzed.

Session Organizer:

Hara Kouki, University of Crete

Chair:

Vasiliki Makrygianni

224. Humans and Animals: Managing Co-existence

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

This panel is an investigation of our new, or renewed, entanglements with animals, whether dolphins, coyotes, dogs, or horses. What does it mean to invent or reinvent our relationships with them? More specifically, when our objectified conception of Nature as a stable and universal entity constructed against Culture melts down, how can we rethink or reimagine our links with the multiplicity of Earth's other inhabitants? How can we create new ways of communicating with animals by considering their own specific manners of engaging with the world? The pandemic was, of course, a good experiment, and made us more aware of their presence, at least for some of them. If our common living resources disappear, how do we negotiate our cohabitation? How do we deal with, or understand, their perspectives, even use them, without discarding them? This panel explores different forms of diplomacy, or mutual understanding, ways of ignoring, or caring, that allow individuals and collectives to survive. Panelists will also interrogate diverse methodologies that take into account these multiple encounters between humans and non-humans.

Participants:

Alboran Sea: A Scene of Friendship and Rivalry Between

Humans & Dolphins *Tarek Elhaik, UC Davis*

In this talk I examine an ongoing debate between fishermen, marine biologists, and environmental activists on the Alboran Sea along the Northern Moroccan and Southern Spanish coastlines. In recent years, fishermen have challenged several port authorities who, according to them, have failed to take measures against bottlenose dolphins (*Tursiops truncatus*) whose repeated attacks damage their catch and fishing nets. This initially isolated phenomenon has now taken on the form of a politically and ecologically volatile assemblage of human and non-human life forms. These debates are primarily concerned with the management of fisheries and halieutic resources in an ecologically threatened maritime zone where resources have become increasingly depleted due a series of factors, from overfishing to pollution. Since both Morocco and Spain are signatories of the Agreement on the Conservation of Cetaceans, striking a balance between regional touristic interests, fishermen's demands, and international agreement has become a delicate act. The paper meditates on these highly mediated scenes of friendship and rivalry between dolphins and humans in the Alboran Sea.

Hazing and Semiosis in Coyote Management Plans *Christopher Kely, UCLA; Chase A Niesner*

Across parts of the US, Municipal Coyote Management Plans have proliferated as documents that address a purported rise in coyote-human interaction, primarily coyote predation of pet cats and small dogs. These plans uniformly promote a practice known as "hazing", despite any ecological or behavioral evidence of its effectiveness, as an alternative to more violent forms of management such as trapping, hunting, and euthanizing coyotes. Hazing involves communicating with coyotes in a threatening manner, often including the use of noisemakers, yelling, using squirt guns, or throwing tennis balls or other projectiles. While the intended effect is to scare off or deter coyotes from killing pets or threatening humans, hazing in fact opens up a novel domain of human-animal communication much different from other forms like pet-training, sign language, or mind-reading. We analyze this form of communication as a form of semiosis that is uncertain for both coyotes and humans, and which can be understood as a present performance of a future state that never arrives, but whose reality is presumed as something to be avoided. Hazing as a practice and a semiosis constitutes an emergent set of relations among humans and wildlife in cities that is related to technically mediated forms of communication including fencing, automated lights, or sprinklers, and the use of cameras, sounds, and scents which form a new domain of human-animal communication.

Diabetics Alert Dogs: The Scent of A Human *Hélène Mialet, York University STS*

My presentation is based on an ethnographic study I am currently conducting in a Californian facility that is at the origin of a new cutting edge "technology" to manage Type 1 diabetes: Diabetic Alert Dogs. Today, this facility is also experimenting to see how dogs can be trained to recognize Covid 19. In my paper, I will follow how dogs' noses are transformed into 'reliable sensors' capable of alerting and giving feedback to human beings about the state of their bodies, in situ, 20 minutes faster than any machines on the planet—a specific form, I argue, of what we call the Quantified Self. If these animals are a necessary (and unexpected) prostheses to maintain human life, their capacity to do so is in part contingent on complex processes that happen at the level of "their fabrication." In my presentation, I will explore the scientific, technical, and psychological processes through which dogs learn how to recognize and anticipate human life threatening factors related to a very specific disease. I argue that the intimate and intuitive knowledge these diabetic alert dogs acquire about the lives they help sustain are crucial to understanding what it means to be human.

Psychic horses, receptive riders: Extra-corporeal communications between horses and their humans *Rachel Prentice, Cornell University*

Equestrian lore describes great riders and horses moving together as one body. Great riding is the art of subtle, often invisible cues. Many riders describe thinking about a move and feeling the horse respond. Scientific research has suggested that this phenomenon is the product of the horse's enormous sensitivity to tactile cues, cues riders often send without any awareness they are doing so. Some experienced equestrians I have encountered while conducting ethnographic research into the relations of humans and horses have gone further: They describe communicating with their horses over distance, detailing a connection that is more psychic than physical (while never denying the power and subtlety of the physical connection). Many of these equestrians have exceptional results, often working with difficult horses no one else can "reach." This paper opens up this level of relating to horses, exploring extra-corporeal communications with horses as a product of the extraordinary sensitization some humans develop with their equine partners.

The Rise of the 'Sensitive' Guide Dog and Cross-Species Care in 1970s Britain *Neil Pemberton, University of Manchester*

This paper historically explores relation-making practices in the context of the emergent assistance animal industry, critically examining cross-species care relations generated through the production of canine guide for people with visual impairment. By drawing upon approaches from STS, animal studies and disability studies, this paper provides a historically-situated case study of what might be referred to as a care-production 'knotting,' where ethics, moral, political, economic and practical orders shape and are shaped by the everyday work of cospecies work. The paper focuses on the operationalisation of a breeding and puppy socialisation programme at Britain's prominent guide dog school during the 1970s. Before its establishment, the guide dog school was entirely dependent on steady supply and careful selection of unwanted canines from dog homes. However, by the 1970s, a surge in demand for guides from the visually-impaired community, with more much diverse needs than previously, raised new questions about the viability of the economy and quality of the dog supply. In response, a coalition of trainers and breeders within the guide dog school overturned the existing regime to establish a breeding stock, which required complex management to enhance and improve canine temperaments and trainability. Nevertheless, a new sensitive guide dog emerged through these relations, but one with a much-reported sensitive temperament, as opposed to a 'tough' one, demanding new kinds of attention and care. How did breeders, trainers, and guide dog owners, who often explicitly referenced a felt desire to care well for dogs, negotiate the tolls of service on a sensitive canine temperament? How and when did discourses of care and improvement inform daily work with this new guide dog?

Session Organizer:

Hélène Mialet, York University STS

225. Doing and Making Times III: Infrastructures

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Participants:

Buildings as makers and doings of time. Two cases from Latin America. *Marco Paladines, Technical University Berlin; Jose David Gomez*

This presentation draws on expectations, temporalities and infrastructures research (Campagnolo, et al. 2019; Harvey, et al. 2017; Joniak-lüthi 2017), proposing an alternative understanding of expectations as interfaces between pasts and futures, and tracing their materializations. We highlight the importance of pasts in future-making, especially in settings shaped by colonial histories, to which STS only recently has offered attention

(Anderson 2017; Kreimer 2019; Lin and Law 2019). Latin America is a generative site for theorizing and for time-oriented STS due to its histories, presents, and creative ways of doing futures. Therefore, we portray the temporal complexity of current sociotechnical dynamics in two cases in Bolivia and Ecuador. Neo-Andean and Transformer are two emergent architectural styles in the indigenous city of El Alto, Bolivia, which aesthetically disrupted the urbanscape and the architectonic expectations in their immediate realm. The practices of design, construction, and use (in/around buildings), as well as the interplay of materials, images, ornamental references and constitutive techniques, propitiates thinking about buildings as infrastructural interfaces between pasts and futures in and beyond the architectural realm. Yachay, the city of knowledge, is a futuristic innovation-oriented city under construction in the Ecuadorian Andes since 2013. From the start, it faced a number of disruptions, breakdowns and struggles around the expectations that first aided in its emergence but now seem to weigh it down. Temporalities of disrepair, maintenance, infrastructuring and ruin have overlapped in the process of designing and building the city, thus generating concrete forms of relating pasts and futures in its infrastructures.

Timely matters and the (un-)making of building futures

Hendrikje Alpermann, Université de Lausanne

This paper traces the socio-material life of an ensemble of empty high-rises, the Hochhaus Scheiben A-E in Halle-Neustadt (East Germany) from the perspective of the (un)making of their (possible) futures between demolition and preservation. Here, building futures are conceptualized as "concretely and materially crafted, enabled, and actively reclaimed" (Ringel, 2014: 68). Looking at their biography through the eyes of the future makes it possible, so the argument, to pay attention also to ideas and projects that have been rejected or not implemented but have nevertheless shaped the buildings' becoming. The purpose of this paper is the exploration of temporal relations and temporalizations involved in the making of building-futures within administrative planning practices. It will be shown how timely matters are made present in planning practices and how they have a transformative effect on the conditions of possibility for the buildings's futures.

Traffic Jams Between Critical Theory and Elementary Physics

Helge Jordheim, University of Oslo

Traffic jams means thousands of people moving, or rather trying to move, in sync, with the unintended side effect that they come out of sync with their surroundings. They cannot make it to work, they cannot eat, they cannot sleep. Excluded from the rhythms of human life, they are stuck on the road, where they should have been driving at extravagant speed. In Critical Theory from Paul Virilio to Robert Hassan, traffic jams have emerged as emblems for a specific dialectics of modernity, what Virilio calls the "dromological law", stating that increase in speed increases the potential for gridlock (Virilio 1991, 65). We humans rarely find ourselves in situations of unintended and unwanted synchronicity. To discuss this rare situation, I will draw on the work by one of the world's foremost traffic-jam scientist, the Russian physicist Boris S. Kerner, who emigrated from Russia in 1992 and started working for the Daimler-company in Stuttgart. For Kerner and his predecessors, going back to the 1950s, traffic jams are simply a part of physics. Every car is considered as an elementary particle constrained to move along a one-dimensional trajectory. This is where this paper starts.

Session Organizer:

Helge Jordheim, University of Oslo

Chair:

Filip Vostal, Institute of Philosophy of the Czech Academy of Sciences

226. Labor 4.0: Algorithmic Management, Working Conditions,

Experiences and Actions of Organization and Resistance

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

The unprecedented economic crisis resulting from the COVID-19 pandemic, the global lockdown, the social distance restrictions, and the sanitary risk have created a breeding ground for an accelerated and unregulated expansion of digital platforms. Big data and artificial intelligence technologies have deepened that path of transformation by automating different spheres of economic, social and political reproduction around the world. Businesses, workers and consumers heavily rely on the use of platforms, services and online work making visible new socio-technical arrangements of the so-called “gig economy.” These new forms of production organization and work management bring opportunities for growth and profit, but also new forms of value extraction and exploitation. Under these conditions, new forms of resistance and organization have emerged in order to bargain the algorithmic labor management methods that companies are implementing. This panel aims to explore the effects of the widespread use of online platforms, algorithm management and other related technologies, and organizational methods in improving or worsening working conditions; and we are also looking for best-practice experiences oriented to the amelioration of working conditions based on fair work principles. The contributions to this panel are open, but are not limited to comparative analysis or case studies of how algorithmic labor management methods impact working conditions; we also seek contributions of how organizations engage on the social bargaining of algorithms, and other social actions aimed at negotiating, reducing, regulating, changing or counteracting those effects of algorithmic management on working conditions.

Participants:

Click And Clean? Unravelling Platform Infrastructure Of Household Cleaning *Anna Pillinger, Vienna University of Economics and Business*

Despite its emancipatory potentials, automation and digitalization of domestic work has not liberated us from the unfairly distributed and mostly unpaid work happening in the private homes. People who want to and, more importantly, who can, outsource their domestic work e.g. cleaning. However, instead of instructing a robot to do these tasks, gig-workers are deployed via labor platforms in a few clicks. What clients oftentimes don't see is how these few clicks enact an algorithmic labor management on each step: selection, review and rating, and finally payment. Hereby, the platform infrastructure, the business model of the companies, the working conditions and the interaction between the different kind of users (clients and cleaners) co-construct each other. This co-construction is scrutinized by conducting i) a netnography, i.e. a “walk-through” (Light et al., 2018) of Helping, the largest German cleaning-mediating platform, and ii) qualitative interviews with clients and cleaners using this platform. We aim to disentangle how these various co-shaping processes a) consolidate exploitation of marginalized groups working in the cleaning sector and, b) change valuation processes in the domain of domestic labor. In doing this we aim to steer a path between the risks and the potentials relating to platform-mediated domestic work – an area seemingly “devalued by default”.

Fostering Flexibility or Promoting Precarity? Digital Labor Platforms and the Danish Welfare State *Konstantinos Floros, IT University of Copenhagen*

Algorithmic management of digital labor platforms and workers' practices to regain control of their autonomy have produced a growing literature on the “gig economy” in recent years. Despite much attention paid to ridehailing and crowdwork platforms, research work on, the less tech-intensive, housecleaning platforms is limited. The state-supported sociotechnical imaginary (Jasanoff 2015) of the platform economy in Denmark is promoted as offering opportunities to businesses and consumers. Platforms operate largely uncontrolled in terms of employment relations, tax issues, algorithmic transparency, and

social dumping conditions. Nevertheless, many workers sign up to them either pursuing -what they term as- more flexible working arrangements or enduring and potentially resisting precarious employment. This paper investigates relations and practices in the Danish housecleaning platform economy, which is characterized by a proliferation of female, young, migrant workers of predominantly Latin-American origin. It engages ethnographically with platform housecleaners aspiring to analyze perceptions that are articulated from below, on both the nature of flexible/precarious working conditions and the role of technology in their consolidation. This study is not limited to platform and app-related features (such as rating, surveillance, algorithm-produced suggestions for customers, profile uploading etc.) but also aims to scrutinize how the Danish digitalized welfare state's policies and infrastructure potentially contribute to workers' insecurity. This paper claims that the double evolution towards an individualization of risk for workers and an individualization of social problems promoted by contemporary digital welfare states creates the adequate political ecology for the proliferation of platform work, within an environment of structured uncertainty.

From Algorithmic Labor Management to Strike 4.0 *Maria Belén Albornoz, FLACSO Latin American Social Studies Faculty*

Technology directly affects the working conditions of those who have chosen digital applications as their livelihood. Workers live in constant tension over customer ratings and how the algorithm processes their performance by assigning them to the next job and calculating the corresponding payment. Far from the utopian futures in which technology is at the service of the worker, today algorithms have built their function within a 21st century Taylorism reloaded. In the case of delivery platforms such as Glovo in Ecuador, the change in the algorithm has directly impacted workers' fees. In 2019, by redesigning the payment calculation per delivery from 1.00 USD to 0.30 USD, by grouping the payment of two deliveries for the value of one, by decreasing the value paid per kilometer traveled, workers' income decreased significantly when performing the same work. This is why “algorithm bargaining” has become the center of the campaign launched by UNI Global Union in September 2020, which has enrolled workers, and labor organizations around the world, in order to negotiate an agreement on the use of algorithms that covers the main requirements for the ethical use of algorithm management to prevent technological innovation from becoming an excuse to introduce mass surveillance in the workplace. The gig economy makes visible the socio-technical systems that underlie these new forms of work. The alliances between technological, social and economic orders highlight the increasingly powerful role of technological solutions for the organization of work in the gig economy. This is why introducing the role of the algorithm in labor demands becomes key to negotiating fairer working conditions.

How Platform Drivers Survive under Algorithmic Management in China *YANI LIU*

Online-hailing taxis has been a prevailing phenomenon in China for years. Chinese platform drivers not only transport people but also feed data into the system to train algorithms and sustain platform's operation and infrastructure (Chen & Qiu, 2019). Most existing studies focused on the platform control issues that drivers faced every day, such as blind passenger acceptance, price surging and rating system to imply platform drivers' working condition. In contrast to a top-down view to conclude platform drivers' difficulties as several general categories, I am more interested in specific problems emerged from dispatching system, working hours counting and rating system in daily practices, and how platform drivers tackle with these algorithmic issues to earn flexibility and make more money. Ethnographic observation and qualitative interviews are two qualitative methodologies I apply to my research. In view of the data

collection convenience, I chose a local platform as the main research subject in my home city, a second-tier provincial capital city in China with more than 4 million residences. Ethnographic observations are based on video recordings of naturally occurring interactions inside the cars for almost hundreds of hours. It will provide insights of the distance between drivers and pick-up passengers, navigation problems of system, car talks with related to their attitudes towards platforms, paying and rating issues. As a supplement, interviews with drivers will also help our understanding of their senses of platform control and algorithmic management that difficult to observe in video data.

Preventing Institutional Power Abuse with AI in the COVID-19

Pandemic *Ömür Yanıkömeroğlu, Middle East Technical University Science and Technology Policy Studies; Arsev Umur Aydinoglu, Middle East Technical University*

Distributing shifts evenly without the help of an AI is a challenging process. Furthermore, the process' difficulty grows exponentially with the increase in number of personnel involved and externalities such as the harsh working conditions of COVID-19 pandemic. Access to such sophisticated software is nearly impossible therefore, neither the preparation nor the crosschecking of shift schedules are handled efficiently due to the time limitations in health institutions. Thus, without any digital solution present, the distribution process becomes open to human bias and exploitation. To address this problem, we have developed a semi-automated workforce scheduling software which guarantees distributive justice with the help of mathematical models and machine learning algorithms. By digitally transforming the biased methods of schedule preparations of three sample hospitals, this study aims to critically analyze possible shifts in power relations of organizational hierarchies and suggest methods for preventing power abuse in organizational medium with the help of sociological theories such as 'structuration theory' and 'social dominance theory'. According to our preliminary findings, many of the responsible health personnel use this gap in supervision by favoring their equally ranked (or aged) peers by prioritizing them with more preferred leave days and assigning them more frequently with paid extra shifts. This inevitably causes decrease in morale, worker fatigue, and tensions among health professionals. The research in biases in algorithms is a hot topic; however, in this study we adopt the opposite approach and employ AI in order to reduce human error, bias, and exploitation.

Under the Apps, the humans!: Behind and beyond the algorithms *Henry Chavez, CTS-Lab FLACSO / Divergence*

The opacity of the algorithmic management technologies on which many platforms operate has contributed to create an imaginary of a high-tech automated industry. Unintelligible and sometimes unpredictable, the embedded algorithms that govern these platforms are the black boxes that manage the daily lives of the gig workers. They assign penalties and rewards to ensure their supply and increase efficiency and quality of service. The result is a kind of liquid Taylorism in which every worker has a planning office and a control system in his pocket, but no workplace and no boss, at least not a human one. However, as several scholars have already shown, most of these new industries based on artificial intelligence and other data-driven technologies still rely heavily on non-automated human labour. Drawing on the daily life experiences of several Venezuelan immigrants working for food delivery apps in Ecuador, this presentation explores the glitches of these new labour management systems and the ways in which these workers appropriate, reinterpret, and modify the technological regime imposed on them by the platforms.

Session Organizer:

María Belén Albornoz, FLACSO Latin American Social Studies Faculty

Chair:

Henry Chavez, CTS-Lab FLACSO / Divergence

227. Crip Politics, Mad Studies, and Bioethics

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

This panel stages a conversation between STS work from Critical Disability Studies and Mad Studies. Papers query key terms in these two fields, including the conflicting status of enhancement and necessity, optimization and cure, as well as autonomy and labor.

Participants:

Exploring the Crip Politics of Biomedical Technologies

Rebecca Monteleone, University of Toledo

As biomedical technologies are increasingly designed and deployed with a focus on optimization, regulatory concerns increasingly revolve around transgressions across the boundary between therapy and enhancement. The commitment to identifying and policing this frontier reinforces assumptions about allowable and unallowable types of being. For the ideal, self-governing able-bodied/minded figure, technological intervention is often viewed as enhancement or unfair advantage. For anyone figured as disabled, deviant, or otherwise non-normative, technological intervention is considered both medical necessity and moral imperative. The arbitrary yet deeply consequential distinction between these two categories, paired with the conflation of technological innovation and social progress, creates conditions under which the same technologies are inequitably distributed, individual autonomy to (not) adopt them is challenged, and pathologized categories come to bear on individuals in oppressive ways. Drawing on feminist science and technology studies, critical disability studies, and empirical work collecting the narratives of disabled people in medical contexts, I argue in this paper that the discourses that undergird biomedical technologies reinforce curative logics while creating an intractable double bind for people occupying non-normative bodyminds. The embodied expertise of Disabled, Sick, and Mad people is undermined while they are simultaneously held individually accountable for managing their non-normativity. Biomedical technologies then become a tool of neoliberal self-governance, often yielding individual benefit while simultaneously reinforcing hegemonic values of bodily autonomy.

Mad Vulnerability: Rethinking Autonomy from the Perspective of Mad Studies *Kathleen Lowenstein, Michigan State University*

Work within critical disability studies and feminist bioethics has argued for a reevaluation of the ways in which autonomy is conceptualized and understood. In particular, both traditions have argued for an explicit interrogation of the way in which structural considerations shape our understanding of and response to questions of distress and vulnerability. However, relatively little work has explicitly interrogated considerations of autonomy from the perspective of Mad Studies, an emerging discipline that seeks to center the historically marginalized perspectives of those identified as mentally ill. This presentation will build on existing critical work on conceptualizations of autonomy, particularly considerations of autonomy from within clinical frameworks, by placing them into conversation with Mad Studies, asking how these considerations change when the historically marginalized perspectives of those identified as mentally ill are centered.

Stenofarms of Life: Real-time Captioning in the Classroom *Yelena Gluzman, University of Alberta*

Discussions of stenography may evoke sepia-toned images of secretaries and typing pools. Yet despite efforts to automate the women out of these technical systems since the 1940s, stenographic work has persisted. Captioners, like pianists, work on chorded, unmarked keyboards; they are found in courts, on closed captioned television, and doing live, "real time" transcription for d/Deaf students in classrooms. Surprisingly, the

way a steno keyboard stroke produces a stenoform (or word) is not standard; each captioner builds this linguistic system for herself, a unique language distributed across a captioners' body, the steno machine, and the cultural spaces in which they circulate. Though an important area of feminist STS foregrounds feminized labor as the invisible work historically driving data and computer science, there is scant STS literature addressing the women who do stenographic work today. The project I present here considers how claims of technological neutrality shaped stenographic work historically, and the legacies of these ideas for contemporary captioners working in D/deaf communities. Using an ethnomethodological approach to recuperate and describe the work of captioners in the situated ecologies of their practice, I show how real-time stenography is done as a form of embodied cultural and linguistic production. This project addresses STS discussions challenging the neutrality and objectivity of information technologies, intersectional accounts of technology as mediating hegemonic social roles, and contemporary STS concerns with the effects of AI and automation on the marginalization of workers and disabled communities.

Session Organizer:

Rebecca Monteleone, University of Toledo

228. Dissolving Boundaries: Creative Practice Meets STS – II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

This set of experimental sessions brings together poets, artists, and musicians alongside STS scholarship and STS approaches in order to explore the role of the nonlinear, the nonverbal, the intuitive, and the gestural in deepening our understanding of climate change, the covid pandemic, and mass extinction -- as well as the scientific response to each of these. The sessions also explore art-science collaborations as a way to generate insight into scientific practice and knowledge, and as a pedagogical method. In addition, some sessions explore not-necessarily-academic knowledge and insight developed via creative interaction with other-than-human beings, as well as through intra- and cross-disciplinary blendings of science, STS, and the arts. Presentations will include readings and performances as well as more traditional inquiry. Session 2 of this panel focuses on music, poetry, art, and performance.

Participants:

Remembering Lost Species *Daniel Hudon*

Of the approximately 900 species extinctions in the last few centuries, most are lost due to loss of habitat, introduction of invasive species or over-hunting. The next big driver for extinction will be climate change as species will have to migrate due to changing environmental conditions and will have nowhere to go. But who are the species lost already? This performance highlights a handful of recently lost species with a reading of lyrical prose pieces that glimpse the animal when it was thriving so that we may better understand what we are losing. The pieces are selected from my book, *Brief Eulogies for Lost Animals: An Extinction Reader*. Portions of the book have been used in a funeral for lost species in Britain, and have been adapted into a play performed in Medford, Mass. in 2019 (and possibly again in Boston, in 2021, Covid permitting). The magnitude of biodiversity loss is as severe as the climate disruption yet this sixth extinction is under-reported and under-recognized. By valuing what we have lost, seeing the crises as connected (for example, restoring ecosystems is important to mitigate climate change as well as improving the interconnectivity of species) we might have a better chance of valuing what we still have.

Shifting Seas *Dee Horne*, University of Northern British Columbia; *Grant Freeman*, Arrowsmith Independent School; *Indrani Margolin*, Associate Professor in the School of Social Work, University of Northern British Columbia

In this panel, four artists collaborate in a creative performance about shifting marine landscapes. Our title alludes to the human impacts that are affecting environments and the need to alter

relationships and prevent or mitigate calamitous consequences. Tereza Jarníková's work in mathematical modelling of the ocean-atmosphere system focuses on the effects of human-sourced carbon increases in the Salish Sea throughout the Anthropocene. She will show the effects of a geochemical baseline shift in these waters - a subtle but critical signal with dramatic effects on the ocean system as a whole. Drawing on poetic traditions of lyrical ballad, elegy and love sonnet, Dee Horne's experimental poem is an elegy about the human impacts on Georgia Strait and also a love poem for the Salish Sea. Grant Freeman's music is a sound collage, using both natural and man-made sounds, that evokes the ebb and flood of tidal currents. He aurally responds to Dee's poem and Tereza's mathematical modelling while Indrani responds through movement. Her dance celebrates water as a source of sustenance both physically and spiritually. This choreography seeks to reflect the dynamic energy of the ocean that gently ebbs and mightily floods to reveal the rhythmic harmony of life and is a dance of love for the Salish Sea. The content and format of our presentation dissolves boundaries between arts and sciences, human and non-human and other false binaries. Using technologies and diverse modes of knowing, this will be an interactive collaboration with each other and the Salish Sea.

To See Clearly *Amy Christine Hassinger*, University of Illinois; *Joy Yang*, University of Illinois

"To See Clearly" is a multi-media presentation involving spoken word, improvised music, and supplementary visuals that explores contemporary fears and perceptions of apocalypse and how we might reframe those fears into a new way of seeing. Essayist and vocalist Amy Hassinger both reads and sings sections of her essay "To See Clearly," (forthcoming in *The Normal School: A Literary Journal*) which uses Johnny Nash's popular 1972 song "I Can See Clearly Now" as a structural touchstone while it explores fear of apocalypse, the history of space exploration, and the visions of the Hubble Space Telescope. Amy is accompanied by the original improvised piano and theremin music of musician Joy Yang. Photographic images from NASA's collection augment the presentation at key moments. The recorded presentation concludes with a joint rendition of Nash's song, performed with an improvised, ethereal spin. In its improvisatory dialogue between musician and writer, music and text, "To See Clearly" embodies a kind of striving toward good relations—with our fellow humans, our technologies, and our planet. Improvisation requires close listening and implicit respect for the others' statements; viewers of the presentation will watch this close listening and response unfold in real time. The piece also directly addresses the widespread fear of the unknown—i.e. climate disruption and its aftermath—that characterizes our current apocalyptic moment, and actively strives to move its viewers past that fear into a sense of openness and creative engagement with our shared future.

Session Organizer:

Christine Wenc, Arts + Literature Laboratory / Greenwood History

Chair:

Christine Wenc, Arts + Literature Laboratory / Greenwood History

229. A Good Life, In Theory: Thinking and Living with Climate Change - III

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

In recent years, an increasing amount of STS and STS-aligned scholarship has used provocative and conceptually creative ways to address the exceptional challenges posed by global climate change. A number of theoretical orientations have emerged within Anthropocene studies, such as new materialism and Gaia-based approaches, offering sophisticated ways for scholars to think through the implications of climate change for both

human and more-than-human life. However, these shifts have also inspired backlash from those who argue that the constant search for new theory obfuscates empirical realities and the politics of responsibility. Particularly in light of the climate crisis, the at-times tenuous and overlapping relationships between theoretical creativity, empirical rigor, and everyday action demand renewed critical attention. This panel seeks to critically engage these fragile relationships within Anthropocene STS scholarship to illuminate potentials for individual, academic, and political meaning in a warming world. How can scholars hold onto both climate realism and creative conceptualizations of more-than-humans? Does the urgency of global warming demand a more overt level of political engagement in academia? Can we effectively reconcile the conceptual utility of our theoretical methodologies with the pragmatic and embodied risks of ecological justice? Papers will address these multiscale gaps, reframing potential discrepancies as constructive spaces of possibility for good relations between fellow earthlings. Session III, "More-than-human Infrastructures," addresses fruitful and frustrating entanglements of humans with more-than-humans and each other within and among infrastructures, both physical and conceptual. From artificial habitats to territory surveillance, technology, conservation, extinction, anthropocentrism, and reflections on hubris and failure serve as creative starting points.

Participants:

Anthropocentrism, Presentism, and the Erasure of the Self:

Historical Method in the Anthropocene *Anin Luo, Princeton University*

STS scholarship on nonhumans has developed ever-more creative ways to try to escape the anthropocentric conceptual frameworks that have long undergirded humanistic and social scientific work. In this paper, I argue that complete non-anthropocentrism is conceptually impossible, particularly in the writing of history. Using critiques of "presentism" in history of science, which rejects the use of present categories to analyze the past, I show the parallels between anti-presentism in history of science and anti-anthropocentrism in STS-inflected nonhuman history. I contend that in repudiating the "humanness" of the human historian and the "presentness" of writing in the present about the past, both movements attempt to deny the positionality of the historian. Drawing on Haraway's epistemological and historical work, I argue instead for a perspectival "humble history" of human-nonhuman engagement that situates the historian and works through their embodiment. This problematization of "anthropocentrism" interrogates the relationship between STS and history and is particularly urgent in light of increasing calls for non-anthropocentric histories of the Anthropocene.

Building Precarity with Hope Practices: Climate Change, Fake Chimneys, and *Chaetura pelagica* *Jennifer Clary-Lemon, University of Waterloo*

As an aerial insectivore, the chimney swift (*Chaetura pelagica*) population has declined over 90% in the last forty years, primarily due to decline in insect biomass, human disturbance, habitat loss, and climate change (COSEWIC 2018). As a result of contemporary forestry practices decimating original habitat of old-growth hollow trees, the chimney swift now shares common habitat with humans in the form of chimneys, tobacco sheds, and wells. Action plans legislated by the Species at Risk Act in Canada guide the building of particular infrastructures when critical habitat of threatened species is damaged. For chimney swifts, this means building artificial chimneys for the birds each time critical habitat, in the form of historic masonry chimneys, is destroyed. Yet the swifts do not tend to inhabit human-built fake chimneys; they are generally a failed experiment in Canada (Finity and Nocera, 2012). These mitigations, refused by the swifts, serve as monuments to both the absence and presence of species extinction and to the difficulty of approaching alterity affectively—getting close enough, for example, to mark either loss of species or desire for future reconciliation. The structures, as complex architectural superpositions of the zoe and bios

(Braidotti 2006), provide sites for reflection about climate change and the "good life." In this talk, I examine three field sites of failed mitigations, suggesting that we might hold them close as creative conceptualizations of relations with the absent nonhuman other as they enact human hubris, embody hope-practices (Head, 2016), and story the Anthropocene through nonhuman bodies.

Extinction in the Anthropocene: The Passenger Pigeon and Ivory-Billed Woodpecker *Pamela Camille Perrimon, Annenberg School for Communication & Journalism, University of Southern California*

Established in 1964, the IUCN's Red List of Threatened Species serves as an index of species health and as all-encompassing biodiversity measure. The database is rife with controversy due to ad hoc growth, relativistic categories, and species inequality. Using the Red List this project concerns itself with what it means for a species to become extinct. Extinction is riddled with inconsistencies and is an evocative and dramatic process inculcated with loss. As such, it is deeply connected to processes of time and memory. Through examining the status of two bird species, the Passenger Pigeon and the Ivory-Billed Woodpecker, I map conflicting examples of extinction within the Red List using historical narratives and contemporary scientific reports to explore what it means for a species to be extinct and how the temporal terrain of extinction is navigated when a species disappears. Where the Passenger Pigeon was among a group of vertebrates listed posthumously, revived after being functionally extinct decades before the archive was founded, the Ivory-Bill is kept alive despite general consensus of its extinction. Where one has been revived to provide a baseline for the archive, another cannot die. I argue that anxiety associated with extinction lies at the core of these disruptions. Liminal species like the Pigeon and Ivory-Bill are trapped in the Red List to circumnavigate the emotional and temporal geographies which extinction operates in. Finally, I challenge that we are in a moment of reckoning with the process of extinction and anthropogenic environmental death that we cannot ignore.

Forest monitoring programs, territorial ontologies, and Indigenous autonomy in Amazonia *Sylvia Rocio Cifuentes, University of California, Santa Barbara*

Forest monitoring programs have become widespread in Amazon basin countries. Using GPS artifacts, smartphones, drones, and other technologies, international environmental organizations propose these programs as tools to control and stop deforestation events—and thus of climate change mitigation. These also seem like ideal initiatives for ENGOs to collaborate with Indigenous organizations, responding to calls to include their knowledges in climate governance (as in Jasanoff, 2004). I analyze forest/territorial monitoring programs created by the Coordinator of Indigenous Organizations of the Amazon basin (COICA) and its member organizations in Ecuador and Peru. While contributions about climate governance in Science and Technology Studies (STS) discuss local/global knowledge, few analyze initiatives on the ground. Conversely, postcolonial STS has yet to fully engage with climate science and knowledges. My methodology incorporates a political ecology of scale perspective and Indigenous research methods, involving open-ended interviews, volunteering, and participant observation with Amazonian Indigenous Organizations. I discuss how monitoring programs are increasingly important for Indigenous organizations to plan, zone, and defend their territories. I further argue that integral territorial ontologies—or conceptions of territories as indivisible entities that encompass multiple relationships between humans and more-than-humans—and Indigenous knowledges influence the objects, purposes, and implementation of these programs. However, Indigenous leaders also raise concerns about privacy and surveillance, as well as about the ownership of (confidential) information. Conclusions therefore discuss the

emancipatory possibilities and the limits of monitoring technologies, as pragmatic climate change initiatives with implications for human and more-than-human life.

Session Organizer:

Amelia Urry, Cambridge University

Chair:

Amelia Urry, Cambridge University

230. Science, Technology and Sport in Uncertain Times

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

Participants:

Behind Closed Doors – Football Under Laboratory Conditions?

Judith Willkomm, Universitaet Konstanz

“Behind closed doors” is where normally football games take place when fans have been excluded as disciplinary measure by the governing body FIFA. During the Covid 19 pandemic the games in the largest European leagues structurally take place without spectators in the stands. This August, the German football manager Ralf Rangnick deemed this situation on German public television as “football under laboratory conditions.” More accurately, this situation resembles a field experiment: due to extraordinary circumstances one factor – football fans in the stadium – is systematically taken out of the occasion, which makes it possible to observe what is missing. In this paper I seize this opportunity to ask a series of questions all concerned with sensory experience and representation. Fundamentally, I ask if and in what way the football game is performed and presented differently now that there are no fans present? But more concretely, it allows us to ask what changes in how the match can be perceived when the verbal instructions of the coaches, the shouts and screams from the players, the clicks of the photo cameras all become clearly audible? In this light it is relevant that Thomas Müller, a player of the most successful side of the 2020 edition of the Champions League, has for his vocal role on the pitch persistently been called “radio Müller” by commentators. From an STS-perspective, informed by German media theory, I will explain how the pandemic situation makes the media-technological infrastructure of the football match visible and audible differently.

Histories of Game Localization Practices *Marina Fontolan; Janaina Pamplona da Costa, Unicamp; James Malazita, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute; Léa Maria Leme Velho, UNICAMP*

Videogame localization is the process of adapting and translating a game to languages and cultures other than the one a game was originally created and is a theme rarely studied by STS scholars. Videogames are the quintessential optical media, as they create different worlds and situations that allow us to mediate our experiences and understandings of our relationships. The presentation aims to debate and understanding some of the past cases of videogame localization. For this, we present data from both Brazil and United States, countries with different videogame industry development paths but with localization playing a major role in its development. We gathered data from different videogame company’s documents available at The Strong Museum of Play (Rochester, NY) as well as documentaries on the history of videogame development. We consider localization as a socially constructed endeavor (JASANOFF, 2015) that allows the technology of videogames to gain plasticity (STAR, 1985) and mediate our relationships both with the virtual and the real worlds. We argue that Science and Technology Studies is an important field of study that enables the scholar to understand how a relationship with technology is socially constructed, concluding that localization is key to allow for developing different relationships to videogames.

How does innovation come about in the bicycle industry? The

case of the “gravel bike *Paolo Magaouda, University of Padova*

In recent years, the “gravel bike” has emerged in the sport cycling world as a new category of bicycle, opening a space between the “racing” bicycle and the “mountain bike”. The gravel bike became one of the fastest growing sectors in the bicycle industry, also bringing a renewal of the meanings associated with sportive cycling. This presentation describes the process of innovation of the gravel bike. Although at least since the mid-‘80s there have been several attempts of hybridization between road bikes and mountain bikes, the construction of the gravel bike as an autonomous category began to take shape “from below”, beginning in 2004-05 with the spread of “grassroots” cycling events in the mid-west of the United States. Then, over the following decade, practices, cultures and equipment characteristic of the “gravel scene” were decisively appropriated by the production and promotional mechanisms of the international bicycle industry, which pushed towards the construction of a new and successful marketing category, which quickly established itself globally. From a theoretical point of view, the presentation adopts an STS framework to discuss the case of the gravel bike in order to question the dynamics of grassroots innovation and the role of users and small firms in the shaping new technical objects. From a methodological point of view, the presentation makes use of participatory online ethnography work in the world of amateur biking carried out over the last few years, complemented by a more systematic search of sources and documents collected through different online research techniques.

To Experience or Escape? The Phenomenology of Urban Cycling *Bernhard Isopp, Munich Center for Technology in Society, Technical University of Munich*

This paper presents a set of ethnographic cases exploring cycling in urban spaces in Toronto, Canada. It starts with the following questions: how do people experience riding a bicycle in a city? Why do phenomena of cycling manifest in particular ways? And how do we get at these phenomena? In pursuing these inquires I take on the challenge of how to combine rich qualitative ethnographic descriptions with various other explanatory mechanisms - not only the familiar terrain of the social, cultural, and political, but also those that are typically explananda in STS - the biological, physical, and ecological. Latent in this framing is a perennial tension: that of reflexive constructionism on the one hand, and reductionism and determinism on the other. In addressing these issues, I suggest that (post)phenomenology offers fruitful insights. While it takes a phenomenon as a causally explainable outcome, it makes no assumptions about what kinds of agency will constitute any phenomena in particular. In this regard, it draws on STS’ novel epistemological and ontological contributions. But it does not shy away from trying to be precise about what determines what in particular cases. The framing of the phenomenon is what allows particular kinds of agency to come into focus without presupposing either too rigid or too indeterminate ontologies. The case of cycling in Toronto offers rich ground to view from such perspectives. By attending to different scales of a complex ensemble of people, places, ideas, and things we can bring into view the different patterns and contingencies that emerge: we find shared experiences of cycling, but also contested visions of the city. These define and are defined by political coalitions with tangible material and environmental effects: where, when, and how the city gets built (and unbuilt). A key focus here is how cycling is variably seen as a means of experiencing or escaping the city, and thus a means of understanding the very boundaries of the urban. I end by reflecting on the normative potential of this analysis.

Twitch and the Work World: Prop Theory Meets “Actual Play” Podcasting *Colin S Stricklin, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Fans of popular transmedia franchises take an active role in the

work of cultural production. Media producers declare their fandom in turn, a show of authenticity and a call for trust and acceptance from audiences. This shared media production-consumption becomes a collective process, and part of Jenkins' convergence culture (Jenkins, 2008). Where production and meaning-making are shaped by ongoing discourse between media, industries, and audiences, we must ask how technological frameworks govern these emerging relationships. Starting from Goffman's frame analysis (Goffman, 1974) and the three-pronged approach established by Fine's Shared Fantasy (Fine, 1983), this essay examines dynamics between player-producers and active audiences in "actual play" podcasts. This genre features play sessions of tabletop roleplaying games such as Dungeons & Dragons, performed alongside an active audience. The argument first reflects on Fine's original frames — social, gameplay, and game world — emphasizing the natural bleed between them. Next, drawing upon Walton's prop theory, it argues that streaming gameplay complicates the work world. This means that streaming destabilizes the canonicity of play, performance, and audience contributions, placing fan works on the same stage as their fan object. Examples from Critical Role and The Glass Cannon Podcast illustrate this effect, tracing cultural performance and active audience participation on the one hand and the role of the platform that facilitates them, Twitch, on the other. This research expands Fine's original categories, calls attention to the technological frame, and argues that the unpredictable currents of convergence culture can be channeled by the design choices of platforms.

Session Organizer:

Jennifer Sterling, University of Iowa

231. Socio-Gerontechnology – Interdisciplinary critical studies of ageing and technology

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Demographic ageing and the rapid advancement of technology – especially digital technologies – are important societal trends. It is becoming increasingly clear that these trends are also interrelated. Digital devices, information technologies and mediated systems of communication increasingly shape the social worlds of people in later life. Digital technologies are also increasingly designed specifically with older people in mind. This raises important critical questions about the interaction of techno-scientific practice with meanings of growing and being old. Such questions, for instance, pertain to ageism in design, tensions between visions of late-life independence versus the surveillance of older people, bricolage in the configuration of care technologies, creative uses of social media and other digital apps by older people, or, more generally, interdisciplinary theorizing about the many intertwinements of ageing and technology. In recent years, such questions have received growing attention by scholars that work at the intersection of STS and Age Studies to understand the co-constitution of ageing and technology. This dialogue is driven by a strong sense for combining theoretical sensitivities with an activist agenda to improve the quality of life and everyday lives of people as they grow older as these become increasingly intertwined with technoscientific objects. For this session, we invite scholarship at the intersection of STS, Age Studies and Gerontechnology that critically explores such intertwinements of ageing and technology in various empirical domains. In particular, we welcome contributions that explore how STS sensitivities can help do old age policies or gerontechnology design differently.

Participants:

Living in anticipated aging futures: regimes of hope and despair in the emergence of senior cohousing in Spain. *Daniel Lopez Gomez*, *Universitat Oberta de Catalunya*

Senior cohousing is flourishing in Spain as an alternative to traditional care homes and home care solutions, which are at the core of a "care crisis". These initiatives are formed by middle-class pensioners who come together to build a housing infrastructures to age-in-community and to collectively manage

their care needs, through mutual aid and solidarity and care services. Drawing on a long ethnographic study of this movement in Spain, this paper explores how various design and social methods and calculative devices transform "ageing well" into a future-oriented and hope-based project. As a result of analyzing the methodological devices at play in the construction process, the paper foregrounds the affective states that are actively created to orient people temporally towards the future and to critically discuss the ageing futures that these communities render possible and impossible. The main objective of these groups is to "self-manage their future", as one of the founders of the movement said. The paper shows that this implies living in anticipated ageing futures of hope and despair.

More responsible implementation of monitoring technologies for older adults in health care settings *Alisa Grigorovich*, *Brock University*; *Pia Kontos*, *KITE-Toronto Rehabilitation Institute*, *University Health Network*; *University of Toronto*

Amid growing awareness of errors and harms in institutional health care settings (e.g. hospitals, nursing homes), artificial intelligence and other types of monitoring technologies are increasingly advocated for improving the safety and quality of care. Population aging, and in particular the assumption that it will make the "burden" of caring unsustainable for future generations and health systems, is a frequently cited justification in media and policy for investment in research and development of such technologies. The discourse around the use of these technologies has been dominated by enthusiasm about their "transformative potential" to improve health care quality, safety, and effectiveness of care. Yet, there have also been concerns regarding "irresponsible innovation," including that "failed" technologies may further threaten the sustainability of the health care system. Given the potential impact of such technologies on older adults, care providers, and systems, there is a pressing need to reflect on the values that underpin interest in implementing monitoring technologies, and how these values can be (re)aligned with the public good. Our purpose here is to contribute to broader efforts across science and technology studies to question the dominant assumptions that underpin development and implementation of monitoring technologies, focusing on their ethical, social, and policy implications. Our review suggests there is limited and inconsistent empirical evidence regarding promised improvements, and evidence that they may introduce new types of risks that may undermine otherwise good intentions with the use of these technologies.

Self-tracking and justification – elderly needing support to enact their will *Niels Christian Nickelsen*, *Aarhus Univeristy*

Self-tracking services are part of a strong trend and normativity allotting responsibility for chronic disease management to elderly patients. Interestingly, this leads to both closer follow-up and monitoring. I explore how elderly patients justify their engagement in self-tracking and telemonitoring services by discussing their propositions and modes of participation (Latour, 2004). Sixteen interviews were carried out with 50+ very ill patients diagnosed with diabetes 2 and suffering from co-morbidity. This material was discussed and expanded at a workshop. The informants are all involved in self-tracking services offered by a municipal health center. Whereas critical sociologists reject self-tracking as a matter of disciplining (Beck, 1993), I propose, to draw on STS sensitivities to explore what is appealing about self-tracking/telemonitoring for this group of elderly. Thus, we may see self-tracking as a matter of vulnerable subjects needing support to enact their will. This draws on Boltanski & Thevenot's notion 'orders of worth', focusing on how subjects morally order actions (2006). This makes a complex analysis and picture of the challenges this group of vulnerable elderly deals with and the intertwinement of this with technology. Based on the empirical material, I discuss four propositions: self-tracking as 'do as is told', 'enacting the will'; 'flexible accountability' and 'periodic withdrawal'. The

conclusion is that there are many ways to benefit from self-tracking. However, there are also indifference, marginalizing and even oppression at stake (Bellacasa, 2017). To interfere with policy, we need more knowledge about what this type of services does to elderly patients' lives.

Surveilled While Wandering: Using Empirical Ethics to Address the Roles of Emerging Dementia Care Technologies
Astrid Meyer, Aarhus University; Anders Albrechtstlund; Stinne Ballegaard, KORA, the Danish Institute for Local and Regional Government Research

Embedded in the Danish research project LIVSTEGN (translates to Signs of Life), this paper aims to develop an ethical framework for the use of surveillance technologies to support care for people with dementia. Focusing on people who, as a result of dementia, have a tendency to wander and get lost, we address how surveillance technology practices intertwine with care practices in a nursing home setting. Our paper relies on a wide array of experiences from people living with dementia, as well as people affiliated with dementia in their personal and professional everyday lives. Through interviews and participatory design based workshops, residents with dementia, relatives and care staff, take on a leading role in terms of identifying ethical and practical issues. This approach allows for trying out and investigating surveillance technologies in ways that remain grounded in the everyday life of people living with dementia. With our focus on lived experiences of wandering tendencies and surveillance technologies, we put forward a framework for using emerging care technologies, based on empirical ethics. Rather than prescribe values, we look at how surveillance technologies intertwine with, and impact existing care values such as privacy, dignity and safety (Pols, 2014; Grosen & Hansen, 2020). The study draws on STS perspectives in recognising the powerful interconnection between society and technologies. In doing so, we make suggestions meant to evoke good dementia care, while simultaneously contributing to how the STS community can address the roles of emerging surveillance technologies in caring for a vulnerable group. Cited: -Grosen SL, Hansen AM. Sensor-floors: Changing Work and Values in Care for Frail Older Persons. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*. 2021;46(2):254-274 -Pols J. Towards an empirical ethics in care: relations with technologies in health care. *Med Health Care Philos*. 2015 Feb;18(1):81-90

Session Organizers:

Alexander Peine

Barbara L. Marshall, Trent University

Wendy Martin, Brunel University

Louis Neven, Avans University

232. Interrupted Processes: Technology, Creativity and Design

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This panel focuses on consequences of technological interruptions in design from STS perspectives, and questions what we lose to these interruptions through feminist lenses. Technology's disruption of the social has long been a topic in STS. Our panel extends this inquiry into technological interruptions in the practice of design where outcomes impact the social politically and economically. Design is often framed in opposition to craft as mental activity versus embodied activity. In contrast to this false dichotomy, we see design as a craft performing in a network of mind, body, tools, and matter. These sympathetic relationships between mind and hands, hands and tools, tools and matter play creative roles in design processes. It is our position that automated technologies like Building Information Softwares and Digital Fabrication Tools in design interrupt this link. These technologies privilege design as a purely mental activity and disregard the role of embodied activities in the process. Designers who use these technologies are constrained by their knowledge and skills. Additionally, whether intentionally or not, these technologies contain and perpetuate biases that then become part of the design process.

What do we lose in creative processes interrupted by automated technologies? What type of biases impact the design process and how do they impact them? How do we frame the creative process of design as a feminist question? We invite scholarship that looks critically into how a feminist lens may help us reconceptualize the creative process through these automated technologies.

Participants:

Computation to Media, Literacy to Fluency: Crafting Interdisciplinary Interactive Pedagogies
Kimon Keramidas, New York University

If we are to consider computation paradigmatically as a media technology, then we must also consider what we mean by media technology. Lisa Gitelman defines media as "socially realized structures of communication, where structures include both technological forms and their associated protocols, and where communication is a cultural practice, a ritualized collocation of different people on the same mental map, sharing or engaged with popular ontologies of representation." From this vantage point, we must consider the knowledge necessary to not only operate computational technologies, but to comprehend deeply the communicative practices, cultural rituals, and encompassing protocols that operate across computational technologies, especially those that are networked, social, and driven by layered and often hidden data. In response to these conditions, this presentation will discuss how computational media must be an integral part of interdisciplinary pedagogies that emphasize the role of these technologies in the generation of narrative and the development of landscapes of interactive experience. Furthermore, these pedagogies must be rooted in the principle that we require more than just digital information literacy, the understanding of the basic operation and utilization of computational media technologies, we require digital information fluency. Beyond use and operation, fluency is a deeper understanding of computational media that allows for the crafting of complex rhetoric and rigorous arguments using computational media technologies at a level that incorporates the social, cultural, material, political-economic, and even ontological implications of these opaque and ubiquitous devices. The presentation will review courses, projects, and other pedagogical experiments from the other and other collaborators as models for ways to approach computational media within STS and across both academic and more public contexts. Lisa Gitelman, *Always Already New: Media, History and the Data of Culture* (Cambridge, Mass: MIT Press, 2006), 7.

Connecting Practices: An Applied View of STS in Designing, Building, Learning
Stephen Verderber, University of Toronto; Chris Trumble, University of Arizona; Ted Cavanagh, Dalhousie University; Arlene Oak, University of Alberta; Claire Nicholas, University of Oklahoma

'Connecting Practices: An Applied View of STS in Designing, Building, Learning' This paper examines temporalities of architectural research in architectural education, and what STS perspectives have to offer design pedagogy. The conventional studio is modeled on a relatively simple understanding of architectural practice, where research is placed before design. In contrast, this paper suggests a model of STS-informed research that occurs 'with' practice. The authors collaborated on 'Thinking While Doing,' a series of interdisciplinary building projects – created in the context of design-build education – that involved architects and engineers as well as scholars from the social sciences/humanities. Under the conceptual model of 'research-creation' (a recently established grant-funding formula in Canada), an ethnographer and social psychologist, along with a philosopher and historian, worked alongside architecture students and professors. Based on the collaborative experiences of this team, the authors argue that this model of research-creation practice has implications for student studio work. Design studies scholars have argued that architects may already practice

a speeded-up ethnography in the process of doing an architectural project (Norman 1999; Ventura and Bichard 2017). Here we consider this in light of the ethnographic analysis of some of the design situations that occurred during the Thinking While Doing project activities (occasions such as pin-ups, desk crits, programming, and working with clients). Reflecting on such moments, as time is 'slowed-down' or at least reallocated in a designerly way, enables us to reconsider conventions and contemplate new possibilities for engaging with practice. We conclude by discussing how these possibilities might be applied to architectural pedagogy, particularly the architectural thesis.

Design as Craft: Drawing and Weaving *Hayri Dortdivanlioglu, Georgia Institute of Technology*

In this essay, I question the role of drawing in the design process within the framework of the doctrine of duality between theory and practice. This doctrine, based on the classical stratification of intellectual and manual labor, sees drawing as a visual expression of a thought in design. In this stratification, drawing becomes the membrane that both separates and connects intellectual and manual strata, i.e., a transition from the form established in mind to the form given to a material. Rejecting this passive notion of drawing and material, firstly, I challenge the doctrine of duality between theory and practice by showing the interaction between Vitruvian concepts of *fabrica* (practice) and *ratiocinatio* (theory) in his architectural theory. I argue that theory and practice are in a dynamic relationship during and after design rather than a symmetrical one. I illustrate this dynamic interaction by analyzing the act of drawing in a design process. Rather than considering drawing as a passive act performed by hands to express the ready-made image in mind, I consider drawing as an action of weaving intellect and manual into each other. As Lars Spuybroek puts it, a draughtsman "draws as if he is weaving," and the stonemason "carves as if he is drawing." (2011, 40). Considering design as craft, I claim that drawing bridges the intellectual and manual labor by weaving pliant architectural elements into a rigid system of fabric.

The time(s) to listen. Textiles atmospheres and material orientations in the design of an exhibition about reconciliation in Colombia *Tania Pérez-Bustos, National University of Colombia*

In this paper I delve into the different material shapes that listening acquires during the design process of an exhibition. The aim of the exhibition was to present a series of audible testimonies related to reconciliation in Colombia, using a combination of textiles crafts with embedded digital components. At the heart of this design process is textile making and the atmosphere that this material practice generates while being handcrafted, an atmosphere that invites an embodied and careful listening. I explore how this atmosphere can be an inspiration for a design process as well as an exhibit device in which the embodied nature of listening is put into question. Throughout the paper I ask how textile materialities, stitched to and enmeshed with digital components, can (or cannot) enable a careful listening to testimonies related to reconciliation. With this examination I aim to contribute to discussions on the role of material making in the orientation of listening as an embodied knowledge practice.

Session Organizer:

Hayri Dortdivanlioglu, Georgia Institute of Technology

Chair:

Vernelle A Noel, Georgia Institute of Technology

233. How to Read the How-to, Part IV: Wild Manuals

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Salomé Skvirsky (2020) defines the process genre, or "how-to"-ness, as "the sequentially ordered representations of making or doing something." Moving beyond the question of replicability in experimentation (e.g.,

Collins 1985), we take inspiration from Skvirsky to invite submissions that explore aesthetic qualities of the how-to genre in knowledge-making practices. Specifically, we want to extend her analysis to scientific and social-scientific manuals. In thinking about objects like field guides, ethnographic textbooks, ecological surveys, personal research journals, archeological codes and conventions, we ask: what kind of affects, attachments and aesthetic experiences are produced and reproduced in the doing of science and through its representation in manuals? Skvirsky focuses on absorption, but we also invite papers that explore other feelings like boredom, love, anxiety, resentment, awe, etc. How are they enabled by the "how-to" genre of the manual? And how does this genre produce, reproduce, and disrupt relations, good or otherwise, between knowledge producers, objects of study, disciplines, institutions, and places? The manual is also a genre of theory seen in the exemplar of J. L. Austin's *How to do Things With Words*, Bruno Latour's *Science in Action: How to Follow Scientists and Engineers through Society* and, to a certain extent, in Kate Brown's *Manual for Survival*. We therefore invite submissions that interrogate a "how-to" manual as an object of analysis, but also as a mode of STS analysis and theorization, or, better yet, written in the how-to genre itself!

Participants:

A User's Manual for E: Method: An Interface for producing topologies of intimacy *George Valladares, RPI*

Pause. This is a manual on asking questions to the tune of magical realism – this is a work of fiction, how to use and make E: Method. "Fictions, in this sense, are not falsehood but refashionings through which analysts experiment with and test different possibilities for creating more just and equitable societies" (Benjamin, 2016). Our sequence: How is the future tested and put into production, especially in communities of Black, brown, and indigenous folks? Our tutorial is a play-through in how to queer deployments of heterogeneous assemblages of methods using an interface called E: method. This paradoxical approach is useful in "identifying new types of data; challenging methodological norms of coherence, generalizability, and reliability" (Ghaziani and Brim, 2019). E: method aims to provide a prototype, a touchstone for reclaiming practices of inspection, especially of data in units of affect. How do data compression pipelines lead from cradle to prison? How do fields of affect standardize our lives? We aim to produce specific affective topologies through questioning how "what appears as an expression of pure theory also implies a methodology praxis" (Ghaziani and Brim, 2019). Allowing us to render preexisting logics and histories in place by sequencing elements of critical phenomenology, intimacies (Weston, 2017), orientations (Ahmed, 2006), Techno-Vernacular Creativity (Gaskins, 2019), infrastructure studies, and comics. These instructions for making and using E: method demonstrate a component towards the mechanics of anticipation: 'sensing in real-time'. This is how to conduct an experiment on the present.

Environmental research infrastructures: a brief field guide to their formation *Andrea Botero, Aalto University / Universidad de los Andes; Karen S. Baker; Helena Karasti, University of Siegen*

Ecological and environmental research are historically based on data collected at designated locations that reflect the characteristics of each particular biome. More recently, however, large scale initiatives building research infrastructures have promised profound transformations in the ways this scientific work is achieved. Both the idea and the challenge of environmental research infrastructures (ERIs), is to assemble, connect and make comparable heterogeneous data collected at various times and at vastly distributed ecological locations. ERIs are intended to bring together data across multiple spatiotemporal scales for collaborative research efforts relating to urgent global problems such as climate change, biodiversity loss, management of natural resources, and sustainability of ecosystems. ERIs information, we have learned, could hardly be described as being

developed through evolutionary trajectories with clear directionality (Pollock and Williams, 2009). Rather their formation appears uncertain and incoherent at times, thus their stability and ability to connect can not be assumed (Jensen and Winthereik, 2013). In this contribution we introduce a series of descriptive, analytical and speculative illustrations, that explore ERIs we have studied and their varied formation processes. The illustrations are constructed in the spirit of a “Field guide”, a format originally intended to assist and speed up the identification of targeted kinds of wildlife for all those interested in nature (Law and Lynch, 1988). The visuals imagined and created, as well as issues presented in them are meant to act as signposts and question markers for us and our research collaborators (scientists, funders, policy makers, general public) by collecting analytical and interventive materials that help us articulate activities and arrangements (Karasti et al 2021). We consider, for example, typologies and the ERIs forms that related communities see, the kinds of development strategies possible, and the potential futures they suggest.

How To Be At Home On The Range *Emma Pask, University of Chicago*

Roy W. Aldrich was the longest-serving Texas Ranger in history. Working from 1915 until 1947 in Austin, he was an avid collector of many things: books, plants, animals, correspondences, receipts, ethnological objects, porn, scrapbooks, photographs, and other memorabilia. Aldrich was also in correspondence with a number of Texas ecologists, naturalists and historians throughout his term as Captain in the Texas Rangers. One object that exists in both his personal archives and in scientific archives is a 1945 issue of *The American Midland Naturalist* published by the UT professor B.C. Tharp. This object exists in at least two parts: the first is a short academic article titled “Noteworthy Plants of Texas I: Three New Species from Texas;” which includes a plant named after Aldrich, *Thamnosma Aldrichii*; the second is a short insert in the same issue entitled “University of Texas Herbarium Biographical Note I.” which thanks Aldrich directly. I am particularly interested in the format of this article: as part of an aspirational manual of Texas’ plants. This imagined ecological study emerges, in part, from the violent paramilitary surveillance projects of the Rangers. This paper therefore examines the ways in which police-work and ecology are co-constitutive in the state of Texas and how they reproduce themselves through the genre of “how-to-ness”. Moreover, this fragment of a never-completed manual is charged with sentimentality in its performance of ecological expertise and its possessive attachment to Texas’ specific environment and I examine the way this does and does not emerge from its manual form.

How-to watch corals die in 90 minutes *Damien A Bright, University of Chicago*

This paper explains the ambivalent structure of *Chasing Coral* and the affective confusion it solicits. The 2017 Emmy-award winning documentary shifts from scientific essay (how-to-know coral biology) to technological odyssey (how-to-feel coral necrology). The result is a process film: not how corals die, but how-to show corals die. The film asks: What went wrong? How did coral scientists spend so many decades documenting, classifying, dissecting, analyzing, modelling, and testing corals only to find themselves, like everyone else, spectators before global reef collapse due to ocean heating and acidification? In answer, it shadows a group of explicitly amateur coral enthusiasts who learn from scientists why corals die and how to track the 2015-16 global mass bleaching event in real-time but do with this knowledge what scientists (allegedly) cannot: document the global oceans’ plight with feeling, not data. What is nature documentary after the “end of nature”? Can climate crisis—a spacetime of epistemic and moral confusion—be filmed? To what ends? What do scientists gain from participating in a spectacle of their own inadequacies? I address these questions

through media and ethnographic analysis. I discuss a pre-screening at a major coral science conference in 2016, filmed for and included in the documentary as its denouement: cinema triumphs over science by aestheticizing the loss of coral as a research subject. I examine how shame mixes with wonder, grief with relief, and climate horror with cinema’s wondrous underwater milieu.

Session Organizer:

Emma Pask, University of Chicago

Chair:

Boyd Ruamcharoen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

234. Open STS Publishing Infrastructures

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

While global Open Access and Open Data movements have argued that publishing data and increasing access to publications will lead to “better Science” as a result of further peer review and possible reproducibility, critics have argued that in fact these versions of “openness” have furthered an academic audit culture without necessarily addressing deeper systemic issues of epistemic (in)justice and diversity (Shearer 2020). Studies have demonstrated how in-built values as well as established norms and practices in scholarly publishing sociotechnical infrastructures skew what is published and by who (Invernizzi 2020). This roundtable brings together STS journals and relevant scholars to reflect on this debate and the often hidden layers of scholarly knowledge production in scholarly publishing to foreground the ways in which day-to-day infrastructural choices shape the production of STS knowledges. We seek discussion about what “openness” should mean in STS, what role publications should aim for in fostering openness, and concrete practices and policies that publications can pursue to meet their aims. We imagine this roundtable leading to a collection of ESTS in 2022, and policy guidelines for implementation at ESTS and other journals. Works Cited Shearer, Kathleen, Leslie Chan, Iryna Kuchma, and Pierre Mounier. 2020. “Fostering Bibliodiversity in Scholarly Communications: A Call for Action.” Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.3752923>. Invernizzi, Noela. 2020. “Visibility of publications from different world regions in nine leading STS journals.” Paper presented at the 2020 Society for Social Studies of Science Virtual Conference, Aug 18-21, 2020.

Presenters:

Lucía Ana Romero, CONICET - Instituto de Estudios sobre la Ciencia y Tecnología, Universidad Nacional de Quilmes
Leandro Rodríguez Medina, Universidad de las Americas Puebla

Salla Sariola, University of Helsinki

Ruth Oniang'o, African Journal of Food, Agriculture, Nutrition and Development

Marcel LaFlamme, Public Library of Science

Alberto Corsin Jimenez, Centro de Ciencias Humanas y Sociales

Anne Pollock, King's College London

Krystal Tribbett, UCI Library

Session Organizers:

Grant Jun Otsuki, Victoria University of Wellington

Amanda Windle, Managing Editor, ESTS

Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine

Chair:

Aalok Khandekar, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad

235. Artificial Intelligence in global perspective: inequalities, changing relations, governance - III

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

This panel aims to generate comparative insights into the ways in which AI technologies are debated, developed, applied and governed around the

world. Developments in AI, machine learning, and big data are transforming societies, the relationships of humans to each other, and interactions with the environment. Simultaneously, the deployment of AI, AI-based robots and smart information systems takes place in a context of global inequalities and competition, as well as well differences in cultural values, political systems and scientific capacities. In this panel we welcome contributions that explore aspects of the following questions: (i) What role do global inequalities and differences play in terms of how AI systems are developed, used and discussed in different global contexts? (ii) Which region-specific and shared global challenges emerge with regard to the governance of AI, AI-based robots and smart information systems? (iii) What are the effects of AI technologies on issues related to equality, diversity, justice and inclusion/exclusion around the world? (iv) What are the implications of the global adoption and use of AI systems for STS, and the ways in which relations between humans, data, intelligent machines and the (social and natural) environment are conceptualised and governed? The panel invites conceptual, theoretical and empirical contributions from across the world, with a particular interest in perspectives from Africa, Asia, the Middle East, Central and South America as well Oceania. Contributions that explore transnational developments or the effects of the international transfer of AI technologies from Europe and Northern America are also welcome.

Participants:

Ethical governance for an environmentally sustainable AI
Gabby Samuel, King's College London; Federica Lucivero, The Ethox Centre, University of Oxford

Data-driven technologies, including the use of AI, promise to make a profound impact on society, and the pace of development is staggering. However, the so-called "digital revolution" has an important environmental and health impact because its heavy energy requirements lead to high carbon dioxide emissions. Furthermore, the reliance on minerals to develop technological components can lead to unsustainable and/or toxic mineral extraction and e-waste disposal. While the environmental footprint of data-driven technologies may be considered unproblematic because of improvements in energy efficiency and the move to renewable energy, the speed of innovation is set to outpace the world's renewable energy sources, leading to increases in carbon emissions when other sectors are decreasing their energy use. Moreover, issues of unsustainable and unregulated mineral extraction/e-waste disposal still remain, creating equity and justice issues, especially because these activities are primarily an aspect of LMICs. Such issues have so far figured only sparsely in both policy initiatives supporting digital initiatives, as well as in recent scholarly literature discussing the ethics and governance of the data/digital revolution. We report on a project that is beginning to fill this gap in ethics discussion. In particular, we employed empirical methods (bibliometric; interviews) to map the available scholarly knowledge on the topic, to identify relevant actors; and to determine the perceived challenges for an ethics governance approach to environmental sustainability of the digital revolution. We report on the findings here.

From copper mining to data extractivism? Data worth-making at the Data Observatory in Chile
Matias Valderrama, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Martin Tironi

The dark skies over northern Chile have been conceived as ideal for observing the universe. That's why some of the biggest telescopes in the world are in Chile. This has led to massive volumes of astronomical data being generated in the country, feeding a socio-technical imaginary of abundance and economic development. The Data Observatory (DO) was created to acquire, store, analyse and extract the value from astronomical data generated in Chile. It was devised as a vehicle to foster Chile's digital economy by taking advantage of the "natural advantages in astronomy" (Arancibia et al. 2018). But the project expanded its focus from astroinformatics to seek to extract globally valuable datasets from diverse sources (observatories, satellites

or the health area), to position Chile as a world leader in data science and AI. We conducted a qualitative case study of DO that involved an analysis of secondary materials and a dozen interviews with relevant actors in the development of DO and current partners (Amazon, Universidad Adolfo Ibáñez and the Chilean Ministries of Science and Economy), as well as critics of the project. In this paper, we describe the friction-loaded institutionalisation of the DO and its techno-determinist discourse around data-centric innovation in which big data is framed as "the copper of the future". We analyse what we call the "mechanics of worth-making" of the DO in which it attempts to justify the value of its datasets by reproducing the naturalisation of data collection (Couldry & Yu, 2018) and the colonial and extractivist logic that has endured in Latin America (Svampa, 2019).

Governing Artificial Intelligence: 'Trustworthy AI' as European Imaginary
Bao-Chau Pham, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies

Despite its ubiquity in public discourse, AI remains an ill-defined term with differing accounts of its future possibilities and risks (Stix and Maas 2020), as well as diverging views about how AI technologies should be governed. In this landscape of competing narratives, the Europe Union (EU) has been crafting the framework of 'Trustworthy AI'. Employing the concept of sociotechnical imaginaries (Jasanoff 2015), this paper will examine the EU's notion of 'Trustworthy AI' and the ways in which it is becoming institutionally stabilised and publicly performed. Specifically, I pay attention to how 'Trustworthy AI' as an imaginary enables as well as constrains particular AI developments while enacting what is considered normative (Rieder 2018). Such a sensibility therefore allows us to explore not only the characteristics of this particular vision of AI, but also the performativities of 'Trustworthy AI' as policy. In exploring how 'Trustworthy AI' is being enacted in key EU policy documents such as the 2020 'White Paper on AI', this contribution sheds light on the (un)desirable futures, hopes, and risk calculations that make up the imaginary that guides and is promoted by the EU. By unpacking the means through which AI is being defined and imagined in the EU context, the paper contributes to analyses of both emergent AI governance and the region-specific characteristics of such governance. It lends itself to comparative discussion of the visions guiding AI policy: how does the EU imaginary of 'Trustworthy AI' compare to governance elsewhere, and how is it travelling to different contexts?

Germany's approach to a human-centric AI
Jens Hälterlein, University Freiburg

With its National Strategy for Artificial Intelligence, published in 2018 under the title "Artificial Intelligence made in Germany", the German Federal Government presents its visions of the future development, application and regulation of AI technologies. With this strategy, the Federal Government is pursuing the goal of making Germany and Europe a leading AI location and thus helping to secure future competitiveness. Moreover, the strategy and other related documents articulate the sociotechnical imaginary (Jasanoff/Kim 2009) of a "human-centric AI". This sociotechnical imaginary not only encodes what is attainable through the use of AI (in terms of technological fixes), but also expresses the normative idea of a political space that provides a certain level of wealth, freedom, security, and well-being to its citizens. In my presentation, I will analyse the articulation and mobilization of the imaginary in political discourse and thereby address three aspects that are key to understanding the sociotechnical imaginary: The concept of "technological sovereignty" and the ways economic competition against the two leading players in AI – the US and China - is framed as a question of competing understandings of technology governance and protecting freedoms, human rights and values. The "ethics-by-design" principle and the ways this principle relates to

normative issues such as trustworthiness, robustness, privacy, transparency, non-discrimination, fairness, and accountability. The standardization and certification of AI-based products and services and the question how these relate to levels of criticality of AI technologies (as proposed in the EU whitepaper on AI).

Global Perspectives on AI: challenges, governance, responsibilities *Achim Rosemann, De Montfort University, UK; Simisola Akintoye, De Montfort University; Nitika Bhalla, De Montfort University; Muhammed Ali Bingol, De Montfort University; Laurence Brooks, De Montfort University; Damian Eke, De Montfort University; Lizette Huezo-Ponce, Tecnológico de Monterrey; Yaseen Jakhura, De Montfort University; Caroline Khene, De Montfort University; Antonia Leach, De Montfort University; Juliana Nnadi, De Montfort University; George Ogoh, De Montfort University; Fatemeh Zarrabi, De Montfort University*

This paper presents findings from a focus group study that explores perceptions on the implications of artificial intelligence (AI) among varied stakeholders in several countries in Africa, Asia, the Middle East and Latin America. AI is expected to transform and disrupt sociotechnical systems around the world, with effects on employment, production, decision making, political administration, the emerging of new forms of social control and surveillance, and many other changes. The ways in which the benefits, disadvantages and risks of these developments are distributed within and across societies will vary, and is influenced by global asymmetries as well as social, cultural and political differences. In this paper we will discuss perceptions and expectations of stakeholders around the world on (i) the ways in which global inequalities and differences will affect the deployment and impacts of AI technologies, and (ii) how they change human relations and lead to new opportunities as well as potential disadvantages and forms of exclusion. We use these insights to reflect on debates in STS on the governance and use of AI, and emerging technologies more generally, and on the ways in which responsibility, care and solidarity can be defined, operationalised and enacted in both, national and international contexts.

Session Organizer:

Achim Rosemann, De Montfort University, UK

236. Non-Extractive Methods for an Extractive World: Indigenous STS and Decolonial Methods

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

This roundtable features STS scholars who are bringing Indigenous STS, decolonial, and anti-colonial values, practices, protocols, and methods to their research in order to produce more accountable, accurate, and responsible scholarship that intervenes in the histories of settler colonialism and the biases of science while activating the possibilities of Indigenous science, technology, and society studies as put forward by Indigenous STS scholars like Kim TallBear and Max Liboiron. This roundtable will discuss how we strive methodologically to be in good relation to ourselves, each other, and our non-human kin. Through guided conversation, we will answer to—How do we understand, dismantle, and counter the work of ongoing colonialism in all of its forms? Who are we responsible to and how do we manifest our responsibilities through our research practices? What concrete practices are we engaged in and how do we decide on appropriate methods? What does it mean to foreground our careers with a commitment to be “in good relation” to ourselves, each other, and our non-human kin? How does bringing an ethic of justice, care, and radical tenderness change our scholarship?

Presenters:

Kristen Simmons, University of Chicago

Uahikea Maile, University of Toronto

Meredith A. Palmer, Department of Science & Technology Studies/ Cornell University

Ashton Wesner, Colby College

Krishna J Hernandez, UC Santa Cruz

Mia McKie, University of Toronto

Session Organizer:

Kristen Bos, University of Toronto

Chair:

Michelle Murphy, University of Toronto

237. Scaling the Ethical Plateaus of Energy Justice - III

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Energy systems are in a state of flux. Climate change, the COVID-19 pandemic, the collapse of oil and destabilized energy economies have forced the world's energopolitical regimes (Boyer 2019) to grapple with new and evolving demands on and for energy infrastructures. These geopolitical shifts signal both emerging windows of opportunity and causes for concern, as the ethical plateaus that have come to define contemporary energy ecologies rupture at their fault lines. The growing set of diverse conceptual complements with which energy is often paired (e.g., energy rights, energy vulnerability, energy democracy, energy transitions, etc.) betray different assumptions about the scales and systems of relevance to energy politics and to processes of sociotechnical change. Energy justice, by contrast, calls for a more holistic view of the ethics informed by unique energy ecologies—i.e. the historically and culturally specific modes of relating to one's self, to other humans, to non-human life, and to the environment through one's relationship to energy and energy infrastructures. This means that more nuanced attention is needed to account for and enact just energy relations in situ. Session #3 “Carbon-Free Controversies” includes studies of the political and ethical conundrums arising out of challenges to develop new, renewable, clean, and/or carbon-free energy systems.

Participants:

Curtailing justice? The distribution of the benefits of Distributed Energy Resources (DER) in Australia *Sophie Adams, University of New South Wales*

As the installation of residential rooftop photovoltaic solar systems expands in Australia ahead of rates of uptake in the rest of the world, the ‘curtailment’ of solar electricity exports presents a new challenge of energy justice. The curtailment of rooftop solar systems and other DER occurs as electricity flows into the grid are cut off in order to maintain stable voltage levels in distribution networks originally designed for unidirectional flows of energy. It also means that the value of the DER that many households, moving into a new role of producing and selling as well as consuming energy, have chosen to install as a financial investment may be considerably reduced - and in some locations more than others. This raises questions about the distribution of benefits and costs in a context in which the renewable energy transition in Australia is being driven in no small part by the private initiative of millions of these ‘prosumers’ as they leverage the affordances of the shared infrastructure of the electricity grid. It is also a context, however, in which these DER owners continue to be effectively cross-subsidised by those without DER, who disproportionately bear the cost of maintaining an electricity system capable of meeting the needs of all. Based on focus groups with Australian households both with and without their own DER, this paper explores how this complex emerging issue might be made sense of and approached as one of energy justice.

#Decolonize4Climate: Beyond an Extractive Energy Transition

Emma Harrison, Stanford University; Adrienne Cheng; Leslie Quintanilla; Amrah Salomon, UC Santa Barbara; Paloma Chavez, UC San Diego; Marlene Brito-Millan
Green, decarbonized, and electrified are new energy paradigms in the movement to replace fossil fuel cars and power plants with battery-powered replicas. In North America, the climate movement has rebranded itself with rhetorical appeal to unions

and labor as well as marginalized racial and low-income communities within settler-state boundaries. This shift has established a “green” identity category that crosses class lines, uniting disparate actors: Tesla-drivers, expert-knowledge producers, social justice organizations, and environmentalists, together urging us towards massive capital investments in renewable energies. The emergence of this market positions the source material supply chain in the interests of national security, bodyguard to economic returns, while sidelining and silencing Indigenous communities whose lands are destroyed along the supply chain. The world’s largest reserves of lithium, a key battery component, are ancient life-giving aquifers in the driest non-polar desert in the world. Pumping subterranean lithium brine into evaporation pools is creating a new sacrifice zone in Northern Chile and Argentina in the name of averting climate catastrophe. Grounded in solidarity with Indigenous water defenders, we question the framework of a jobs- and energy-centered “just transition” that leaves colonial/capitalist extractivism intact. As natural and social scientists, we critique the axiomatic use of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change report and its ahistorical focus on carbon dioxide and temperature to motivate large-scale—but not truly radical—climate action. We turn instead to decolonization and abolition as methods for climate scientists, activists, and educators responding to the long disaster of climate colonialism. We propose #decolonize4climate as a conversation for the now.

Energy Justice For Whom? Ethical Plateaus of Lithium Extraction and Electrified Transportation *James J. A. Blair, California State Polytechnic University, Pomona*

Worldwide, the power generation and transportation sectors are two of the largest sources of air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. One way to mitigate these harmful impacts of climate change is by transitioning to clean energy generation and zero-emission transportation options. Such green technologies currently depend on lithium-ion batteries, which require minerals. Besides other minerals like copper, nickel, graphite, manganese and cobalt, lithium is a key component of lithium-ion batteries that store energy for electric vehicles, smart devices, and renewable power plants. Although lithium is present all over the globe, one of the main commercially viable reserves is in the Puna de Atacama, a borderland desert region shared by northern Chile, northwestern Argentina, and southwestern Bolivia. Drawing on collaborative and engaged research sponsored by the Natural Resources Defense Council (NRDC), this paper interrogates how the reliance on brine evaporation as an extraction method for lithium mining is exacerbating conditions of ecological exhaustion and limiting water availability in the Puna de Atacama. It draws on ethnographic field research with environmental activists, Indigenous leaders, international scientists and policy practitioners. Leveraging this transnational framework to think through the broader ethical plateaus of lithium mining and electromobility, the paper considers emergent problems inherent to global energy justice. It discusses contradictory social relations of “extractive renewables” that become apparent when scholars and advocates attempt to jump scales from conflicts over lithium production in South America to grassroots campaigns for a just transition through electrified transportation, as well as new lithium mining proposals, in North America.

Minerals for Just Energy Transition: A New Conundrum *Nidhi Srivastava*

As several countries embark upon a journey to low carbon pathways, the actual and sustained energy transition is dependent on availability and accessibility of raw materials needed for renewable energy and energy efficient technologies. It is estimated that energy transition will be extremely mineral intensive since clean energy technologies require more materials than fossils (The World Bank, 2020). In the last few years, scholars have tried to engage with the theory of justice in energy

and transition. McCauley et al have defined energy justice in terms of distributional, procedural and recognition justice (2013). The concept has been expanded to include restorative justice to correct the mistakes of energy sector (Heffron & McCauley, 2017). The discourse on just energy transition has revolved around minimising negative impacts on people dependent on fossils or ensuring greater employment opportunities in renewables or low carbon sectors (IISD, 2018)(Tsani, 2020), but not on the impact of critical mineral extraction needed for such transition. Minerals and Energy have been treated as two distinct sectors, in policy as well as academia, neglecting their interdependence. Justice in energy transition has been viewed in a very localised context, one of ensuring justice for people getting affected by decarbonisation in terms of losing jobs due to a shift from fossil fuel. While intergenerational aspect is integrated, inter jurisdictional aspect is not discussed, especially when energy transition in one jurisdiction is completely dependent on raw material from another jurisdiction. The proposed paper argues for extending the domain of energy justice to go beyond a narrow interpretation of decarbonisation, and extend to securing raw material for energy transition.

The Social Construction of Solar Information Systems *Brian Sutherland, University of Toronto*

Accelerating climate change is creating infrastructure uncertainty where societies are required to evaluate and adopt more sustainable energy systems rapidly, while addressing energy inequality to create a more sustainable world. This work examines a number of historical periods through the lens of the social construction of technology, where artifacts, narratives and social imaginaries were concerned harnessing organic energy flows to power information infrastructure, specifically by means of solar energy. Referring critically to past STS oriented histories around power generation artifacts, I will examine this new collection of solar material artifacts, the social and often colonial context and values around their creation, designs and intentions for use, marketing contexts and methods, instructions introducing solar operation, cultural references around their use, patterns of wear in their appearance and operation, collector communities, their presence in professional conservation institutions, and what these artifacts suggest about designing sustainable communities. Solar power and its potential for decentralized energy challenges the dogma of centralized power generation all over the world. What can the history of solar design teach us about a sustainable lifestyle and achieving certainty and justice around energy?

Session Organizer:

James Adams, University of California, Irvine

238. The Prediction Factor: Medical Decision in the Age of Big Data - II: Concerns about the prediction factor: regulation in question?

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

The introduction of Big Data in the health care setting raises particular concerns with regards to accuracy, bias, responsibility, equity, exclusion, safety and privacy that this session will address. This session will include a discussion that will focus on the papers’ proposals in terms of social, medical and ethical regulation of predictive analysis.

Participants:

AI in Medicine: from Expert Systems to Deep Learning and Algorithm-driven Health Care *N. Elida Defurth, York University, Canada; Renate Baumgartner, Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen; Vassilis Galanos, University of Edinburgh*

Abstract The present paper aims at highlighting the historical processes underpinning contemporary excitement about artificial intelligence (AI) and algorithm/data-driven innovation in healthcare. We focus on the tumultuous trajectory of AI’s hype

and disillusionment and its social construction (as well as negotiations about its validity as a pure pattern); the lessons or potential pitfalls from the international arenas of second-generation AI (roughly between the mid-1980s and late 1990s) which may benefit contemporary adopters and vendors in and around medical practice. How much can we learn from the disillusionment following the enthusiasm with knowledge-based expert systems? What did we learn from DARPA's Strategic Computing Initiative? What was the legacy of the European Union's ESPRIT programme? What examples are there to date that show AI and algorithm/data-driven innovation in healthcare has still a long way to go to be ethically sound and produced to gain health equality/equity? We draw from historical and contemporary literature as well as our empirical research to shed light on issues of classification, accuracy, and in/equality in currently proposed AI technologies for precision medicine. By doing so, we aim at offering initial glances towards a responsible framework, informed by STS approaches, currently missing from existing debates around responsibility/accountability.

Algorithms, Children and Mental Wellness at School *Anne-Elisabeth COURRIER*

During the pandemic, children's Education have been highly disrupted, forcing the US state districts to provide laptops to students and develop e-learning. However, US districts wanted to ensure that children were using these computers properly. In particular, school districts needed to arrange that first, children were focused on their assignment and assessments and second, that children did not access unauthorized websites. For so doing, districts partnered with tech companies for applications which could help districts and teachers to, remotely, prevent fraud and monitor students' activities on school devices. Such applications enabled teachers or district officials to remotely supervise students screens 24/7 from classrooms or district offices, even after school hours or on weekends. Promoting "real safety in real time", some companies such as Gaggle developed new products able to "warn against violent threats" or to alert about some students' mental health issues and harmful behavior, such as bullying, self-harm, and suicide and suggest partnering with therapists in case of violence or suicide prediction. This raises some legal and ethical concerns: speaking about a child, is it prevention or intrusion? Safety or privacy? What are the consequences of the predicting factor in flagging a child for behavior? What are the legal protections? What about the consent? what fate for this data in the long run? Are predicting factors of children mental wellness really a way to "strive towards good relations"?

Am I Blue?: The Affective Training of Wearable Emotion Monitors *Heather Nolan, University of California - Davis*

In her book on facial recognition technology, *Our Biometric Future*, Kelly Gates asserts that biomonitoring devices work "to make human affective behaviors more calculable, to open them up to precise measurement and classification, thereby making them more amenable to forms of intervention, manipulation, and control" (22). Feel is a wearable biomonitoring wristband that "continuously detects and monitors your emotional state." CEO George Eleftheriou suggests that Feel helps users "better connect with" themselves, their loved ones, and the world. Feel promotional materials draw on affective computing, where computers use facial recognition, movement, and voice analysis to make determinations about human emotion to generate AI with both affective qualities and an ability to react to human emotions. Feel, though, monitors physiological processes - temperature, movement, Galvanic skin response - which it translates into emotional states with help from users who feed information about their mood to the app. In this talk, I argue that devices like Feel, meant to monitor mood, normalize the surveillance of affect. Drawing on affect theory and media theory, my close reading of the Feel device, app, and website demonstrates that this normalization happens through the

strategic deployment of the metaphors of affective computing, encouraging users to help train computers to more effectively track emotional states. It also has the effect of altering the way we define emotions, promoting qualitative measurements and computing analogies as central to understanding human feelings and interactions, and thereby posing important questions central to STS about the limits of data for understanding the human.

Session Organizer:

Adeline Perrot, Ethox Centre - University of Oxford

239. Power in Relation: Digital Technologies Across Geography and Scale

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

As scholars of technology, data, and the digital, we analyze phenomena that are not confined to a distinct scale or locale. At their core, our empirical objects are relational and inter-scalar. As such, we employ methods to trace unravelings across purported centers and peripheries, between nations and industries, and with differential effects on "different social groups [that] have different relationships to anyway-differentiated mobility" (Massey 2012). Drawing on postcolonial, feminist, and transnational geography insights around place and space, and specific conceptual inspiration from recent calls in geography for relational comparison (Roy and Robinson 2016), in this panel we examine the materialities and imaginaries of technology as a "multiplicity of interconnections" that bound consequences across sites and actors. In this session, we draw out productive comparisons across scales and locales to explain the relationship between technology and governance, citizenship, everyday survival, and assumptions / inevitabilities about how to create better worlds. We integrate these insights into the ways that STS scholars have long used place-based research to gain new insight into agency and technology (e.g. Hecht 2011; Lindtner 2020; Murphy 2017 Tsing 2005; 2015; Wajcman 2014). Specifically, we are interested in reopening questions around "the local" and inhabited space, with regard to what makes technological interventions spatially meaningful, even where tenets of scalability/transferability abound. Accordingly, we investigate materiality, infrastructural labor, and the political economy of technology as it moves, with particular attention to how space is used and categorized in the wake of tech deployment, regulation, and use.

Participants:

The Art of Quantifying the City *Burcu Baykurt, University of Massachusetts Amherst*

Many U.S. municipalities increasingly work with data analytics companies that help them build and maintain urban big data. Yet little is known what services these companies provide and how they translate various municipal data into policy decisions. Drawing on interviews with data analysts, this paper documents how urban data analytics companies try to cultivate and exploit computational expertise in local governance. While placing themselves among tech giants, municipal agencies, and community groups as epistemic brokers, urban data analytics firms, on the one hand, make a concerted effort to access and extract value from municipal data and seek to offer a coherent area of expertise that solves local problems by data. On the other hand, they often reach beyond hard numbers to imbue datasets with new meanings in order to tailor their services and solutions for specific cities. Drawing on feminist STS and feminist geography, this paper argues that urban data analytics are not a straightforward attempt to quantify a place and rationalize local policy decisions. Social relations, local histories, and instabilities of a place also shape the possibilities and limits of seeing the city through data.

The Geopolitical Shaping of Racialized AI *Till Straube, Goethe University Frankfurt; Seyram Avle, University of Massachusetts Amherst*

In March 2018, CloudWalk Technology, a Chinese AI company, signed a 'strategic partnership' with the Zimbabwean government to deliver facial recognition technology for security

and law enforcement in the African country. While both parties emphasized financial applications and security uses, local civil society groups, international media, and academics speculated that the true strategic goal is to train the CloudWalk AI on a substantial Black population via free access to government data to build competitive advantage on a global scale, given the global discourse that current AI is biased against dark skinned people. This paper takes the case of CloudWalk in Zimbabwe as a problem space in which to investigate the complexities and contradictions of AI training and race in the broader frame of geopolitics and global techno-capitalism. Specifically, it examines how race and ethnicity come to be embedded in AI systems in peculiar ways across geographies and the varying socio-cultural, political, and economic systems that shape their adoption and use. Based on this, we posit a typology of harms that occur at these complex intersections.

Domestic “WFH” Customization and Feminist Theorization of Space and Technology *Margaret C Jack, Syracuse University School of Information Studies; Ingrid Erickson, School of Information Studies, Syracuse University*

This paper uses the case of independent workers, working in customized spaces in their homes, to address the question: how can we (or should we) re-theorize the gendered dimensions of space and technology when work and life are joined, both spatially and in practice? Feminist geographers and STS scholars have long disassembled an oppositional and hierarchical notion of space, pointing out the falsities inherent in the conception of a dominant public male realm of production (the city) and a subordinate private female one of reproduction (the home) (Blunt and Rose, 1994). These faux divides between public and private, patriarchal and capitalist, have, instead, been inverted to visualize the value of domestic work, often feminized and rendered invisible, as integral to functioning infrastructures (Star and Strauss, 1999; Suchman, 1996; Wajcman 2009). We use the empirical case of domestic customization by workers to analyze the continued power of such binaries as the public/private, user/designer, and domestic/paid work, and, in the process, shed light on the cultural assumptions related to gender roles, workplaces, and demarcated space that are still very prevalent in our society. Our analysis suggests that domestic customizations often represent investments of unpaid personal time, space, effort, and resources to enable paid work. As such, they raise new questions about domesticity and productive labor that prompt new thinking about the intersection of gender, labor, and space (Suchman, 1996; Star and Strauss, 1999).

Theorizing Data-driven Deliberation *Ritwick Ghosh, New York University*

Both data and deliberation are considered important for public policy, yet they also represent conflicting sources of authority. In this paper, I examine how data-driven governance contrasts with ideas of deliberation and participation. The distinctions are explored in the context of US Farm Bill policies. Rural sociologists and historians have shown how the implementation of US Farm Bill policies reflects a struggle to balance participatory with hierarchical modes of governance. What is less clear is how the struggle is being reconfigured by recent references to data-driven governance. Drawing on over 70 interviews with US agricultural policy practitioners, I analyze how data-driven governance is performed and unraveled at the center (Washington DC) and at the peripheries (North Dakota). The research shows how the concept of data-driven governance masks important deliberative work, and thus political negotiations – both in DC and in field offices. I propose the idea of data-driven deliberation as an analytical tool to explore how references to data can both enable and constrain forms of deliberative governance.

From Evidence-based to Data-driven *Leah Horgan, University of California, Irvine; Kavita Philip, University of British*

Columbia

In this paper, we ground the evolution of the smart city in dominant ideas and practices in Development. In bridging the smart city and the development economics lab, we suggest that the movement to become a data driven and smart city is inherited not from silicon valley innovation, but from specific, pro-Development discourses and machineries: The same modes which now seek to regenerate many Western cities are rooted in the past decades of Development experimentation on Global South peoples and places. Drawing on a two-year participant observation study with the Los Angeles City Data Team and related artifact analysis, we trace the material and epistemic infrastructure of data-driven smartness to three specific legacies: (1) a particular shift in development economics toward microeconomics and the empirical, and the use of randomized control trials (RCTs) to evaluate poverty alleviation programs and generate evidence-based policy (see: de Souza Leão and Eyal’s 2019); (2) the exaltation of Silicon Valley innovation culture, and with it, the rise of tech for good logics and techno-philanthro-capitalists such as the Gates Foundation; and (3) the increasing dependencies of cities on ever riskier streams of capital for planning and development purposes (see: Goldman 2010). The purpose of highlighting these links and lineages is to question what we mean when we speak of smartness and data, as the move toward evidence-based policy making on the one hand, and the present moment of algorithmic, data-driven governance on the other, collapses important epistemic distinctions between evidence and data.

Session Organizers:

Margaret C Jack, Syracuse University School of Information Studies

Leah Horgan, University of California, Irvine

Burcu Baykurt, University of Massachusetts Amherst

Discussant:

Megan Finn, University of Washington

240. Technologies of Death and Dying at the Beginning of Life - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Technologies of Death and Dying at the Beginning of Life The advancement of reproductive technologies has not only made an impact on how life emerge; technologies also remake death and dying at the beginning of life. In fertility clinics surplus embryos raise questions regarding if, when, and how they can be discarded or used for non-reproductive means. Ultrasonography used for prenatal diagnosis situate expecting parents in situations of whether they should terminate the pregnancy when fetal malformations are detected, and infants some time die even though technologies are used to keep them alive. Moreover, new technologies are developed in regards to handling dead bodies. This includes post-mortem diagnostics or the development of cooling technologies, such as the cooling cot, a technology that may enable new bereavement practices. In this panel, we welcome presentations that explore in which ways technologies are part of death and dying at the beginning of life around the globe, by asking: How are technologies of death and dying regulated, practiced and lived with? How do technologies impact when a life is deemed killable and grievable? How do processes and conceptualizations of death and dying alter as technologies are increasingly involved in reproduction? How do parents or the medical staff involved, live with the deaths that emerge with technologies? And what are the theoretical implications of rethinking technologies of life to also focus on technologies of death? Finally, we welcome reflections on the politics of ontology, and conceptualizations of technologies of dying, as death at the beginning of life is explored. Potential topics include: technologies of death and dying, grief, infant death, abortion, reproductive technologies

Participants:

Minimally Invasive Autopsy – navigating uncertainties of death
Halina Suwalowska

In recent years, global health practitioners and policymakers have been confronted with the complex challenge of identifying and quantifying the causes of death of the world's poorest people. In order to address this cause-of-death uncertainty and to minimise longstanding sensitivities and reservations about full autopsies in the Global South, funding bodies such as the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation have advocated minimally invasive autopsies (MIA) as an alternative to investigate child mortality. MIA is a technology that involves using hollow needles to collect samples from key bodily organs. It has the potential to be more acceptable and less invasive than a full autopsy, which requires opening the cadaver. While the global development and introduction of MIA is growing, little attention has been paid to the ethical implications of its introduction in the Global South. In this paper, I employ empirical data I collected to demonstrate various social and ethical challenges in the implementation of MIA in the Global South. I show that while MIA technology has been introduced as a solution to this enduring cause-of-death uncertainty, the development and deployment of technologies such as these always constitute interventions in complex social and moral worlds, and, in this respect, are both solutions to and causes of new problems. Therefore, MIA inevitably creates new kinds of uncertainties that need to be addressed. I deconstruct the ways in which these different dimensions and levels of uncertainties have been articulated, experienced, and approached, and the ways the uncertainties relate to each other.

'To Say Goodbye, You Need to Say Hallo' - Memory Technologies, Bereaved Parenthood and Fetal/infant Grievability. *Anna Sofie Bach, Aalborg University Copenhagen*

While infant mortality has significantly decreased during the 20th century in the Global North, death at the beginning of life is not uncommon. Many wanted pregnancies end in spontaneous abortion and, due to increasing prenatal screening, a significant number of expecting parents terminate pregnancies based on the discovery of disease/anomalies. Though rare in Denmark, full-term babies also die in the womb or during birth. Within the past decades, Danish practices around death at the beginning of life has changed significantly. In contrast to the previous 'best practice' of removing the fetus/baby without the parent(s) seeing it, bereaved parents are now incited not only to see the child, but also to touch it, hold it and even bring it home for a few days if they wish. Coining the term 'memory technologies', this paper explores how sociotechnical practices are reshaping the ways death at the beginning of life is handled and understood. Based on an ethnographic study, including interviews with Danish bereaved parents, I follow the institutionalization of 'cooling cots', an emergent technique to slow biological decay, and 'angel octos', a pair of tiny, identical crochet octopuses offered to most bereaved parents in Denmark (one for the parent(s) and one for the child). Through these examples, I discuss how fetal/infant grievability and bereaved parenthood are reconfigured through the sociotechnical practices of memory making and how visibility of reproductive loss reshapes how death at the beginning of life is lived with.

"Conceived child" and hegemonic posthumanism. Ontohegemonic struggles and "Women Strike" in Poland. *Andrzej Wojciech Nowak, Philosophy Institute Adam Mickiewicz University*

As a theoretical background paper combines experimental practice (Papadoulous), ontological design (Nold) and multiple ontologies in practice (Mol) to expand a notion of an 'ontological imagination' (Nowak) and to create STS-inspired support for active onto-political interventions. Through the analysis of hegemonic struggles in Poland, I would like to show that posthumanism can be both insurgent and hegemonic. In a paper I will analyse the role of the "conceived child" (catholic newspeak for foetus) as an object around which political and hegemonic

struggles are waged. The talk will examine the materiality of the hegemony of Women's protests in autumn 2020 in Poland against banning of abortion and the right wing hegemonic response to it, which is a nationwide banner campaign. These banners, ubiquitous in the Polish landscape, feature various visualisations of foetuses designed to reinforce the Catholic ideology of the 'conceived child'. The obtained result is the concept of an ontohegemonic object (such as "conceived child"), i.e., a material manifestation of ontological policies as key actors in the establishment of ontological policies. The outcome will be a proposition of framework for ontologically and materially oriented studies of hegemonic processes.

Technologies at Heart – the remaking of death, at the medical frontier *Stine Willum Adrian, Aalborg University*

The development and implementation of prenatal diagnostics, and the cardiac surgery options for infants and newborns, enable an increasing number of children with congenital heart defects to survive and live with their chronic disease. At the same time as technology help to let live, the technologies likewise take part in remaking death, at the beginning of life. Although advances have been made in regard to pediatric heart surgeries, the future prospects for the children with severe diagnosis are uncertain. Before deciding whether an infant should undergo surgeries, parents are informed that their child is in risk of dying, during or after surgeries. Moreover, the child will face neurological damage on a continuum from learning disabilities, to being severely brain damaged. These technological possibilities will place expecting parents, having their foetus diagnosed, in the dilemma of either deciding to terminate the pregnancy, or carry the child to term. In this presentation I ask: How does the emergence of death in fetuses and infants with severe congenital heart defects, reconfigure and change, as technologies has altered the potentialities of life and death, and how does these deaths affect the parents lives over time? Methodologically, I address this question through what Barad (2007) has termed as diffractive readings. With this methodology I have collected stories regarding severe congenital heart defects mainly stories of infant death including: Interviews with parents that have ended a pregnancy or lost a child, web material, media stories, documentaries, and medical documents.

Session Organizer:

Stine Willum Adrian, Aalborg University

Chair:

Laura Louise Heinsen, AC Meyers Vænge 15, 2450, Copenhagen SV

241. Research-Creation: Milieus without Borders

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

What can membranes teach us about good relations? Membranes facilitate and prevent exchanges between and among milieus. Membranes take many forms and temporalities: they testify to the origins of cellular life; they enable movement and flux; they are opened to external pressure; they consume and produce energy; they metabolize. Membranes are also sites of containment, struggles, wars, and borders. Membranes capture, imprison, eat, digest, and eliminate. This panel will explore the notion of membrane as a concept, a technical object, a site, a trope, and a living analogy. It will explore the regimes of visibility, economies of collaborations, and politics of manufacturing that condition the ways in which a membrane can act as a catalyst for the creation of a milieu, rather than as the border for the protection and defence of a claimed/owned territory. The discussion will focus on a research-creation project, *Membranes in Action*, and more specifically on one of its concrete instantiations, the art installation *Fossilation*, recently exhibited at the Pompidou Center. Research-creation is a methodology that poses problems to the politics of knowledge production by problematizing "issues through practice," and by addressing the "critical grasp of the process" (SSHRC). Situated half-way between an "institutional operator" and a technique, that is, it is half-way between "a mechanism for existing practices to interface with the neoliberalization of

art and academics” (Massumi & Manning, 2014) and a practice capable of overspilling this troubling alignment. Fossilization will thus be problematized as a method, a practice, and a technique capable of resisting the professionalization and instrumentalization of artistic activity, on the one hand, and the “prototyping of new forms of collaborative activity,” (Massumi & Manning, 2014) on the other. The shared objective will be to render visible the social, aesthetic and political dimensions necessary to resist the transformation of milieus into borders. The panelists, whose profiles range from STS, arts & design, engineering and media studies, will discern the social and political implications of this creative process by mobilizing a variety of techniques: architectural renderings, drawings, sketches, as well as audio-visual materials.

Participants:

Practices of Visibility in a Precarious World *Alice Jarry*,
Université Concordia; Brice Ammar-Khodja, Concordia University

In 2018, less than 9% of the resources produced globally found a second useful life. During the same period, human activity will have required the use of 93 billion tonnes of materials and natural resources, 85 billion of which are said to have been extracted from the ground (Montréal, 2019). While the linear model consisting of extracting, producing, consuming and discarding is proving to be more and more distributed and delocalized, the geographical and temporal scale of the socio-environmental phenomena which accompany the future of the technical objects that we create often remain imperceptible to the immediate human sensory field (Parikka, 2015). How to enhance the visibility of such processes? The Fossilization installation (Centre Georges Pompidou Paris, 2021) is a bioplastic membrane and an interactive light apparatus powered by a residual energy capture system that feeds on the museum’s infrastructure. Based on the forms, instruments, spatiality and processes that support this artwork, this paper examines how this membrane links and activates new modalities of sustainable engagement between technology, materiality, humans and ecological milieus. Following its materials (Ingold, 2015; Lange-Berndt, 2015), the project will be approached in the light of the technologies and principles that it advances, such as Design for disassembly; bio-composite materials; and energy recycling. Taking a sensitive and critical look at extractive practices, the research-creation configures an ecosystem that composes with different dimensions specific to its immediate environment. The paper will examine how this work mediates invisible issues by proposing a form of aesthetic, political and critical vigilance of harmful practices, and how it builds a reflection and a dialogue about material imaginaries in a context of ecological crisis.

Mediating Materials *L Wilkins*

Prolific systems of mass manufacturing serve as a filter for the objects we can make, and influence outcomes of the design and fabrication process. This paper examines manufacturing systems as sites of mediation between ideas and objects. Manufacturing acts as a membrane between ourselves and raw material resources that limits and amplifies certain methods of making, materials, and techniques. Manufacturing can often be perceived as mundane or neutral, however, it is an infrastructure that is both a “force-amplifying system (Peters, 2015)” and by their very nature, are systems that fade into the background (Parks, 2005). This makes vast and established manufacturing an incredibly powerful force in imagining what our world can look like. Some items are cheaper or easier to make a certain way because of established systems of production. Over time, it becomes increasingly difficult to disrupt the ways we fabricate things, as dominant technologies take a foothold that is hard to overcome (Winner, 1980). These concealed forces carry with them embedded biases and contradictions. Designing objects is a negotiation between cultural, and social, marked with intended purpose, meaning, and an already specified relationship to the world (Balsamo, 2011). These forces of production will be theorized with methods from the Fossilization Membranes In

Action installation.

Practicing Enjoyment: Happiness without Progress *Marie-Pier Boucher, University of Toronto Mississauga*

In a context where meritocracy and competition are fostered by academic institutions, what kind of research is worthy of good relations? What kind of practices and techniques can intensify the life of collaborations? What modes of gatherings, occasions of encounters, and forms of togetherness can give rise to feelings of enjoyment? Can research-creation alleviate institutional burdens and give rise to joyful experiences? This paper explores good relations at the intersection of institutions, collaborative practices, and domestic life. In contrast with -and not in opposition to- Sara Ahmed, who asks “what does it mean to be worthy of happiness?” and “how happiness justifies oppression?” (Ahmed, 2010) this paper interrogates how enjoyment can be practiced as a technique rather than a promise. Can enjoyment concretize as an act of auto-affectation rather than in virtue of a normative and restorative practice? Can we invent forms of well-being that do not reify a social script of marginalization? Can a diagnostic of killjoy research come with the power of the performative? What kind of hacking techniques can modify institutional life? Departing from an understanding of enjoyment as process rather than a characteristic, that is, as an autonomous “self-creation” (Whitehead, 1929) understood without external reference, this paper will discuss the methods deployed, mobilized and invented by Membranes in Action and the Fossilization installation as a location by which to rethink the economy of joyful collaborations.

Session Organizer:

Marie-Pier Boucher, University of Toronto Mississauga

242. Forensic Evidence And Expertise In Local, National And Global Contexts - III

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Forensic evidence is collected, analysed and rendered meaningful by different actors using various technologies and expertise. A powerful resource in the investigation of crime, STS scholars have paid substantial attention to the development, standardisation, enactment and use of specific forensic technologies (namely fingerprinting and forensic DNA profiling). These accounts demonstrate the complex expertise and labour involved in producing and using forensic evidence, and the many local and national contexts that impact on how the legitimacy and value of specific types of forensic evidence are negotiated over time. Beyond fingerprinting and DNA, there are many other types of forensic evidence. Some have long histories, like fibre analysis. Others, such as digital forensics, are newer and continually evolving, keeping pace and responding to the latest technological developments. In this panel, we invite papers that examine empirically the varied actors, labour and expertise involved in the production and use of other types of forensic evidence in the investigation and prosecution of crime. We are particularly interested in accounts that engage with how forensic evidence and expertise are negotiated in specific local, national and/or global law enforcement contexts and the related areas of overlap and convergence. This panel contributes to STS scholarship on the intersections between science, law and law enforcement, standardisation in scientific practice, and the negotiation of expertise across the different epistemic cultures of criminal justice systems.

Participants:

Wildlife Forensics *Alyse Bertenthal; Simon A Cole, Univ Of Ca-Irvine*

While there is now a robust body of STS literature on conventional forensic techniques like DNA profiling and fingerprinting, less attention has been given to less commonly used techniques such as those in the emerging, interdisciplinary field of wildlife forensics. Laws regulating wildlife trade such as the Endangered Species Act and international agreements such as the Convention on International Trade in Endangered Species of Wild Fauna and Flora grant legal protection only to some

species, and thus provide tools to prosecute takings of plants and animals only in some cases. To effectuate the law and promote protections for wildlife, investigators and prosecutors increasingly rely on wildlife forensic science. Although comparable to human forensics, wildlife forensics differs in a key respect: rather than match a specimen to a specific individual, it instead aims to identify the species to which the specimen belongs. Dealing with unfamiliar plant and animal subjects, new research questions, and an array of disciplines, wildlife forensic practitioners struggle to establish general and generalizable standards that will allow wildlife forensic analysis and conclusions to meet evidentiary standards and be defensible in a court of law. Through analysis of wildlife forensic research and reporting, we ask whether and how forensic practice works differently when the object of analysis is a non-human subject. By examining the emerging field of wildlife forensics, and by comparing it to STS research about human forensics, we gain insight into a new forensic culture, and how it is produced, contested, and maintained.

“Boliden killed my son”: assembling transnational environmental victims in the Arica Victims v. Boliden Mineral case. *Patricio Flores, University of Warwick, UK*
How does forensic work proceed when it is necessary to prove environmental crimes committed by transnational corporations? Despite the internationalization of environmental offences in the context of a global economy, and the consequences it has for vast groups of people, especially in the Global South, STS research on the production and mobilization of forensic evidence tends to be focused on the challenges involved when proving damages experienced by particular individuals as a result of conventional crimes. This paper seeks to address this gap by analyzing the victimization devices used in the context of a recent lawsuit submitted by people from Arica, the northernmost city of Chile, against the Swedish corporation Boliden Mineral, which was accused of damaging people’s health by sending around 20,000 tons of toxic waste to Arica in the mid-1980s. Specifically, and based on interviews and document analysis, the article focuses on two specific devices mobilized in the context of the trial - toxicological data and personal testimonies-, emphasizing how they are assembled in a manner that makes possible the enactment of transnational environmental victims that deserve recognition and redress. Finally, the paper reflects on the challenges faced by plaintiffs when taking toxicological data and testimonies from their original location in Chile to the forum where the case was discussed -the Court of Skelleftea, in Sweden.

Explosiveness, Corporeal Sensibilities, and Forensic Expertise in the Colombian War Landscapes *Julia Morales Fontanilla, Rutgers University - New Jersey, USA; Diana P Pardo Pedraza, The George Washington University*
Serranía de la Macarena was a crucial scenario of military actions in the armed conflict in Colombia. In this region, the Army and FARC-EP guerrillas widely deployed aerial bombardment and improvised landmines as warfare technologies. These devices kill and mutilate bodies, and penetrate and scar rural landscapes. In this context and anchored in our respective fieldworks—a demining project and a state morgue—we ask: what can the explosiveness of these military technologies tell us about how experts sense, locate, and temporalize the materiality of war? In this presentation, we will probe the sensorial emergence of forensic expertise. How do morgue workers and rebels turn demining-experts learn to sense war? This is an ethnographic, collaborative, and experimental exploration of evidential retazos [snippets] that we found and collected in La Macarena: pieces of cloth and leather, fragments of metal embedded in trees and dead bodies, severed human corpses, or residues scattered in broken ground. Others are bits of conversations that took place amid practices in the morgue or minefields. Contributing to STS

conversations on forensic science and the materiality of evidence, we argue that techno-scientific local engagements with these retazos illustrate corporeal sensibilities developed to perceive the traces of war. To sense the war is to notice traces that may be imperceptible to others (i.e., ethnographers), and to give an official account of those indications. These retazos speak about what it is and what it means to endure war, live despite the war, and make life out of the war.

Medical Knowledge Against Medicalized Killing:
Contemporary Forensic Counter-Expertise on US Executions by Lethal Injection *Nicolas Fischer, CESDIP, University of Versailles St Quentin*

Drawing on the study of legal documents and on a series of interviews, this communication will study the social production and activity of a specific group of medical experts: physicians or scholars in anesthesiology who got involved in critical expertise over the practice of penal executions by lethal injection in the USA since the early 2000s, and who now regularly appear in the media and before court to challenge the alleged “humanity” of this execution method. The presentation will first adopt a situated, non-essentialist perspective on expertise to describe the making of this group of “improbable experts”, whose main field of study is external to forensic science, but who unexpectedly engage in counter-forensic practices and strategies. This group is a small and coherent one – a dozen professionals – with connections to a global network of lawyers and anti-death penalty activists that will be closely analyzed. Second, it will focus on the technicality of the counter-expertise these specialists produce: to challenge the narratives of “correctional” experts who describe lethal injections as painless, they draw on a range of methods including the analysis of injection protocols, of blood samples collected on executed inmates, and the autopsies of their bodies. The communication will examine the experts’ struggle to perform these analyses in closed-in correctional realms, and the different forms of scientific “truth” they produce on the executed body and its reactions. Finally, the presentation will examine the legal consequences of this expertise, as it moves from public statements to testimonies before court.

Session Organizers:
David Wyatt, King’s College London
Dana Wilson-Kovacs, University of Exeter
Chair:
Dana Wilson-Kovacs, University of Exeter

243. Nonhuman Phenomenology and Technoscientific Intersubjectivity - 2: Other Affinities

1:20 to 2:50 pm
4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:
Cultivating Soilkin: Phenomenological Exercises with Soil and Stones *Alexandra R. Toland, Bauhaus Universität Weimar*
In the thought-provoking essay “About a Stone: Some Notes on Geologic Conviviality”, Hugo Reinert (2016) poses the question: “What modes of passionate immersion – or love, or intimacy could a stone afford?” Drawing on ideas from multispecies ethnography and science and technology studies (e.g. Tsing, 2011; Puig de la Bellacasa, 2015; Kirksey, 2014), this essay and series of accompanying exercises link Reinert’s research in the far north with kindred stones that have journeyed from Sámi territory in Norway to the end moraine landscape of the Biosphere Reservation Schorfheide-Chorin, just north of Berlin. The “Soilkin project” proposes a series of relational, performative exercises that engage with current geontological discourse (see Yusoff, 2015; Povenelli, 1995) to encourage reflection on the individual and collective agency of mineral and more-than mineral others and the boundaries of what it means to be alive. Critically unpacking historical concepts of soil science

and agronomy, the “Soilkin project” argues that 1) a non-normative understanding of soil subjectivity could lead to kinship – soil kinship – with appreciable social and phenomenological qualities that expand current human-soil relationships; 2) soil formation (pedogenesis) can be interpreted as a process of learning and becoming rather than simply weathering and aging; and 3) soil agency is situated within a framework of resistance and consent, demanding that the terms of kinship between humans and soils be mutually beneficial and appropriate to the slowed-down timescale in which soil beings live and operate. The paper includes performative components, locating the research at the interface of STS and Artistic Research.

Questioning the “Intelligence” of Superintelligence *Tertia Gillett, Villanova University*

Artificial intelligence has the potential to greatly improve human life and society, but it also poses a significant existential risk. Due to the potential threat posed by powerful superintelligence, it is important to ensure that they are moral, friendly to humans, and concerned with human values. Proponents of superintelligence acknowledge that “value-loading” is a significant concern and suggest different ways that values might be encoded into or acquired by AI systems through direct coding, machine learning, emulation, and so on (Bostrom 2014). My contention is that important notions about the ontological and morphological possibilities of minds, bodies, and social structures are imprinted into these systems long before the question of coding is relevant. How we conceive of intelligence is conceptually prior to epistemological and ethical questions of risk assessment. In this paper, I focus on the highly anthropocentric notion of intelligence that plays a key role in AI research. Specifically, I address the problem of understanding cognitive capacities and intelligence strictly in relation to the ability to solve problems that are exclusively human. This has important implications for AI development and STS because these systems may not themselves be recognizably human. In addition to the risks of reifying existing social inequities, we should examine our assumptions about the size, composition, and interests of minds that are much different than our own. I conclude that our biased and limited idea of intelligence restricts our capacity to design or identify intelligent non-human systems, and this has serious conceptual and socio-political implications.

Reassessing perceptions of self, sex, and kinship in evolutionary biology through the study of chimerism in nonhuman primates *Rachel Voyt, The University of Texas at Austin*

Evolutionary biology has long been conflicted in its treatment of the “self” within its theoretical paradigms. While evolution as a process is an inherently population-level phenomenon, the conventional language and culture imposed on evolutionary theory by Western scientific ideals remain fixated on an ideology of competitive individualism. Complicating this focus on individualism, however, is the widespread presence of chimerism and microchimerism in human and nonhuman bodies, particularly among mammals. Through the transplacental bidirectional transfer of cells during fetal development, as well as through tetragametic fusion or the absorption of twins in-utero, individuals can contain DNA from not only their “self”, but also their mother, their siblings, and potentially others. This mixing of DNA not only troubles the traditional biological categories of “self”, but considerations of biological sex and kinship as well. In this paper, I explore how the study of chimerism and considerations of identity in nonhuman bodies may complicate traditional theory and inform the production of new theory within evolutionary biology. I focus specifically on callitrichine primates – small-bodied monkeys from Central and South America – as a case study. These nonhuman primates are unique in that nearly every individual may exist with not only transplacental microchimeric DNA, but regularly occurring hematopoietic chimerism from chorionic fusion with their twin siblings in-utero. Drawing from feminist and queer theories of

science, I assess the current literature on callitrichine chimerism, its applications to human biology and identity, and the potential ramifications for current models of evolutionary theory and practice.

Session Organizer:

Richard Fadok, MIT

Chair:

Claire Isabel Webb, University of Southern California

244. Techniques, Technologies, and Relationships in Mapping Evictions

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Creating and maintaining “good relations” of sociotechnical and political nature are key goals of community-led mapping. Good relations, however, are difficult to cultivate in the face of political urgencies, especially with rampant evictions and racialized dispossession accelerating throughout the COVID-19 pandemic. In this panel we discuss the challenges of collaborative research for housing justice. As members of the Anti-Eviction Mapping Project (AEMP)—a volunteer-based feminist collective that produces maps, tools, and narratives to support the work of housing justice— we explore what it means to work beyond the boundaries of academia and the non-profit industrial complex to conduct community-led research. We place this work in conversation with key topics in STS scholarship, including “knowledge co-production,” decentering of accredited expertise, valuing community-led design, open infrastructures, and questioning power dynamics in expert fields that too often drive away those committed to housing and racial justice, nevermind feminist, abolitionist, and decolonial politics. To address relational tensions from multiple perspectives and infrastructural needs, we will engage the following: - Good (enough) relations: challenges of working across class, gender, race, ethnic, expertise divides and inequities in community-based cartography; - Collaboration in contexts of accelerated temporality, ephemerality of online relations, and finitude (finding, supporting, and losing collaborators); - Project boundaries, interpersonal interactions and inclusion dynamics: tensions in political formation and onboarding of members from corporate or academic sectors; - Dynamics of open technologies and protection of digital resources: challenges of creating alternatives to surveillance platforms; - Critical design methods and practice: facilitating community-led outcomes, counter-mapping/storytelling, radical inclusivity, and decolonial approaches.

Participants:

Black Exodus, creative cartography, and the limits of counter-mapping Black geographies *Adrienne R. Hall, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill*

The devastating push out of Black communities from San Francisco has been chronicled in myriad ways from local government reports and news articles to stunning visual art. Most accounts index the decline of Black San Francisco through census data, typically with 1970 marking the height of the city’s Black population (13 percent) and 2010 marking a startling low (6 percent). Through these storytellings “Black Exodus” (re)emerged as a popular shorthand that evokes visceral responses while crafting a depoliticized framing of systematic displacement as an issue of Black “out-migration” from California’s cities. Aware of the violence that plotting another map of Black loss might reproduce, in 2016 members of the Anti-Eviction Mapping Project (AEMP) turned toward arts-based storytelling to trace Black histories, cultural production, and social movements amidst ongoing racialized dispossession in America’s most gentrified city (Allensworth, Hall, & McElory, 2019). Three years later AEMP released (Dis)locations: Black Exodus as a limited-copy print zine that aimed to balance the finitude of “Black Exodus” by thinking about the past, present, and possible futures excerpted from oral history interviews, art, and textual reflections. This paper reflects on (Dis)locations: Black Exodus alongside a 2017 provocation about the problematics and possibilities of maps/mapping technologies in

representing Black life (Nieves, Kim, Nesbit, Carter, & Johnson, 2017, p. 2). In particular the paper considers the limits of presenting Black geographic life through the political technique of counter-mapping; searching for a Black cartographic imagination; and the imperative of “good relations” for linking storytelling to justice-work.

When 'Open' is Still Far from 'Good Enough': the work of critical mapping with open technologies *Luis Felipe Murillo, School of Data Science, UVA*

What does "openness" mean for the work on digital tools and infrastructures for housing justice research? In this paper we discuss the existing corporate dependencies and the challenges of designing open technologies for housing justice research. This question is particularly urgent in the context where big tech companies are unleashing new geospatial technologies to track and surveil the pandemic, often with little concern for data protection and privacy. Free and Open Source projects for critical cartography have been developed by several collectives to advance both social research and housing justice work, but very little collaboration between STS researchers, FOSS developers, critical cartographers, and housing organizers has been fostered. The goal of moving away from corporate platforms is perceived as urgent, yet, the distribution of expertise and access to digital infrastructures and tools imposes great difficulties for the most vulnerable, poor, and racialized residents for the purposes of housing justice. In order to address this issue, we will describe the experience of AEMP in developing open tools for collaborative mapping during the COVID-19 pandemic and reflect on the hard challenges and technopolitical possibilities for reimagining, creating, and supporting open tools and infrastructures that are more aligned with the goals and needs of housing justice research.

Community-led Design for Housing Justice: Navigating the Tension Between Carefully Crafting and Rapidly Responding *Brett Halperin, Human Centered Design & Engineering, University of Washington*

“We have a saying: ‘Move fast and break things,’” writes Mark Zuckerberg in a letter to investors ahead of Facebook’s IPO in 2012. With this motto, destructive design methods formed the basis of the business as it catalyzed gentrification in the San Francisco Bay Area along with other rising technology giants at record speed. If “fail fast” design “sprints” with glorified “rapid prototyping” fuel the kind of mass “disruption” that neoliberal technology startups champion, then what does it mean to move fast and not break “things”? In this paper, I investigate this question from a design justice lens in context of the COVID-19-induced housing emergency, arguing that the delicate practice of community-led design is at diametric odds with the urgent instability of housing inequity inflamed by the pandemic. By conducting Research-through-Design (RtD) of the Anti-Eviction Mapping Project’s COVID-19 Housing Protection Legislation and Housing Justice Action digital interactive map, I conclude that community-led design tied to the slowness of social change is incommensurable with the rapid rate of harm that structural inequality inflicts on low-income communities of color. While conscientious codesign methods discussed herein extend the work of community organizers and tenants, they struggle to keep up with the pace at which profit-driven entities “move fast and break things” such as the homes of families at risk of a lethal virus upon eviction. This paper explores the tension between carefully crafting a design to support housing justice movements and having no choice but to rapidly respond to a life-and-death housing crisis.

Landlord Technologies of Dispossession and Tenant Technologies of Housing Justice *Erin Mariel Brownstein McElroy, The University of Texas at Austin*

Covid-19 has exacerbated racialized housing injustice and racial capitalism globally. In response, there has been a growing

movement to cancel rent and evictions, facilitating numerous housing court blockades, rent strikes, and mutual aid networks. Yet landlords often claim to feel “threatened” by this tenant justice movement, and in response have opened the floodgates of technological solutionism, using novel technologies to surveil and evict tenants. As I continue to explore, landlord tech, while alive and well prior to the pandemic, maintains a long history of exploiting crises to augment its scope. While landlord tech employs algorithms and AI, it also employs a deeper history of private property itself functioning as a technology of racial dispossession. More often than not, today’s landlord tech is paternalistically implemented under the auspices caring for tenants, but instead privileges care for buildings and their value more than those living within them. Here I explore landlord tech’s pandemic expansion as it implements novel surveillance technologies into domestic space. From biometric cameras controlling building access to AI tenant screening processes, I outline the new modes of seeing that landlord tech implements. At the same time, I explore housing justice collectives’ utilization of maps and software to flip the gaze back upon landlords themselves. New tools such as the Anti-Eviction Mapping Project’s Evictorbook are enabling tenants to study landlord property portfolios, eviction histories, and webs of shell companies. Platforms such as this support multi-building organizing work and the broader movement to abolish rent.

Precarity by Design: Tenant Oral Histories in the evolving terrain of “eviction moratoriums” *Maria Velazquez, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

COVID-19 has exposed how housing functions as healthcare and the precarious state in which those who rent homes are found across metropolitan regions (Alanya et al., 2020; Aurand et al., 2020). Prior to the pandemic, evictions, houselessness, and drastic housing burdens were prevalent, particularly for minoritized communities, single-mothers, elderly, and folks with disabilities. COVID-19 has only exacerbated the existing housing injustice for renters, built upon legacies of housing discrimination, segregation, income and wealth inequality, foreclosures and the commodification of housing. Moreover, racialized systemic policies that excluded access to home ownership, destroyed and under-developed affordable housing, and more recently, enabled wall street investment in housing. In contexts of the pandemic historical moment, the AEMP Tenant COVID-19 Oral History Project was developed to document the struggles and resilience of tenants. This paper examines the tensions in the collection of oral histories within the varied and unequal landscape of eviction moratoriums and fight for tenant protections. Particularly in light of escalating landlord harassments, concerns for crushing rent debt, and growing evictions (despite eviction moratoriums) raising concerns for procedures to protect tenants, sharing of tenant stories in light of escalating landlord harassment (such as tenants facing lawsuits). These tensions arise as we collect oral histories, seek to connect tenants with tenant organizations and resources, and in our collaborative efforts with tenant organizers to mobilize tenant oral histories for systemic policy pushes.

Session Organizer:

Erin Mariel Brownstein McElroy, The University of Texas at Austin

Chair:

Luis Felipe Murillo, School of Data Science, UVA

Discussant:

Catherine D'Ignazio, MIT

245. (Dis)Trust in Public-Sector Data, Technology, and Science - III: Census, Technology, and Numbers

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

STS scholarship on technopolitics typically examines the role that

governments and state organizations play in producing, enabling, and leveraging data, technology, and science. Technocratic projects like conducting censuses, modeling weather, producing medicines, constructing computers or developing weapons serve both state and scientific masters. While the legitimacy of these investments are often intertwined with the legitimacy of state power, such power—and legitimacy—also relies upon scientific development and the sustained production of technoscientific imaginaries. Yet recent years have witnessed a range of governmental actions around the world designed to purposefully delegitimize states' technoscientific investments. Politicians work to dismantle state-funded scientific efforts, often under the guise of free-market commitments and austerity principles. The Covid-19 pandemic has revealed the global cost of distrust in public-sector science, technology, and data. Even as scientists produced a vaccine with unprecedented speed, governments around the world failed to track the spread of the virus, let alone provide data to enable decision-making. In some countries, political leaders are propagated conspiracies and “fake science”, undermining public health and scientific development. Just as governments can help advance science, technology, and data, they may also choose to strategically curb such pursuits—or actively undermine their legitimacy. This panel examines how public-sector technoscientific efforts are made legitimate, and how that legitimacy is strategically undermined. We ask, how are state-sponsored science and technology projects legitimated? How can this legitimacy come undone? How can trust in public-sector technoscience be repaired? This third of three panels focuses on population census and trust in numbers.

Participants:

“Filling in the Gaps”: Investigating Civil Society Organizations' Role in the 2020 United States Census *William Clyde Partin, Data & Society Research Institute; Cristina Maria Lopez Guevara, Data & Society; Emma Margolin, Data & Society Research Institute; Charley Johnson, Data & Society Research Institute; danah boyd, Microsoft Research / Data & Society*

The decennial Census is among the most complex technoscientific projects undertaken by the federal government of the United States. Data collected through this process are not only the basis for the appointment of political power and the disbursement of federal monies but also inform the activities of many governmental and non-governmental agencies. But census data – like all data – are the result of social processes. Moreover, census stakeholders, from partisan agents to civil society organizations, are keenly aware of the contingency of census data and have often sought to shape the process (and its outcomes) to advance their interests, noble or not. For example, members of Census Counts – an ad hoc network of civil society organizations acting in partnership with the U.S. Census Bureau – have played an active role in the 2020 decennial census, seeking, in their words, to deliver a “fair and accurate” count. Drawing on participant observation and 42 semi-structured interviews with Census Counts and other census stakeholders, we describe (1) how these organizations understood concepts of “fairness” and “accuracy” and (2) how those understandings informed their attempts to remake, repair, supplement, and, in some cases, subvert the data infrastructure envisioned by the Census Bureau. In describing the complex, contested, and often contradictory relationships and imaginaries among Census Counts and the Census Bureau, we develop the concept of “gap work”: a dual process by which (data) infrastructural stakeholders construct an (as of yet) unrealized “whole” and then undertake efforts to fill in the perceived “gaps” in that whole.

Reaching the "Hard to Count." Trusted Messengers and the Effort to Avert a Census Undercount *Hannah Obertino Norwood, University of Chicago Crown Family School of Social Work, Policy, and Practice*

Even before the Covid-19 pandemic, the United States 2020 decennial Census was steeped in a sense of crisis in Chicago, where the threatened inclusion of a citizenship question caused worry about the effects of an undercount on federal funding and

congressional representation. Beyond Trump administration actions, an intersecting mistrust of data and government collided to make the Census seem a perilous technocratic project. This paper draws on a year of ethnographic fieldwork following the coalition of organizations, elected officials, and activists that mobilized in Chicago in an attempt to avert an undercount. Of primary concern to these working groups and “Complete Count Commissions” was how to reach groups that the Census Bureau designates “hard to count.” I explore how, in the context of the strategic campaign to dampen census participation amongst immigrants at the federal level, these groups attempted to restore trust and increase counts through a reliance on “trusted messengers.” I build on STS scholarship that has demonstrated quantification to be laden with power and affect and highlighted the racialized figure of population as a site of state intervention on behalf of futures (Murphy 2017). Bringing census digital outreach and advertising into dialogue with ethnographic fieldwork, I argue that discursively down-scaling government and speaking through the figure of the trusted messenger became the means to legitimacy for census counting. In so doing, I engage the 2020 Census as a technopolitical project leveraged simultaneously for anti-democratic exclusion and expanding access to political participation in the service of imagined US futures.

Quieter, powerful and uncontested: implications of methodological changes in population censuses *Byron Villacis*

What are the effects of the increasing digitalization of population registers and the systematic abandonment of traditional population censuses around the globe? While the transition to digital technologies appear as an inescapable next step in the methodological renovation of censuses, this discreet transition leaves unexplored the study of its implications. The literature objectifying censuses has been focused on the problematization of inclusion/exclusion of questions, the legitimacy of the operation, its role in the exercise of state power, and the implications in the production of technoscientific imaginaries. However, there is less attention trying to detect the repercussions of the methodological switch as a whole: from a physical, visible and contestable operation, to a digital, silent, and discrete one. This paper contributes to this debate by identifying material and symbolic consequences of this change and interpreting the implications for subsequent scientific production. The study contributes to the understanding of quantification and standardization expanding the comprehension of mechanisms behind silent processes of inscription, translation, and enrollment; developing analytical elements to understand official statistics as black boxes, which help to control projects from a distance. Methodologically, the paper takes advantage of the crisis of the COVID-19 that provoked public justifications to change the census methodology in the United States, Spain, Colombia, Mexico, and Ecuador. Through archival methods, text analysis and in-depth interviews, I document, compare and analyze statements of offices in charge of the census that support the decision to modify or justify changes from traditional formats to digital versions of the census.

Faith in Australian numbers: personal and institutional networks of trust in public data *Samantha Vilkins, Australian National University*

Little in modern political life is not processed through statistics. Rote nationwide collections are conflated with administrative miscellanea, scientific research and economic estimates as they are used as evidence and rhetoric for public debate. Such numbers gain power through interwoven processes of scientific and political legitimacy — processes made suddenly more visible last year. When Australia's Chief Medical Officer was questioned early in 2020 about international coronavirus data, he declared: “The only numbers I have total faith in are the Australian numbers.” A seemingly odd choice of word, but the

phrasing and sentiment proved well-founded as the pandemic unfolded. Not only was Australia a world leader in their data-led COVID-19 response, but the legitimacy of their numbers relied on a network of both personal and institutional trust with roots traced back to the country's founding. Despite this success, issues in data management later became national controversies as their legitimacy was deconstructed and weaponised in state-politics. This paper draws on interviews with public servants, academics, journalists, politicians and others reflecting on their role in the production of public data. It contributes insights regarding how we conceptualise uncertainty for public statistics, and the dissonance of those who know firsthand the complex social production of numbers yet hold to the pervasive and persuasive perception of their mechanical objectivity in maintaining their authority. Conducted throughout Australia's early COVID-19 response, the interviews also illustrate the mundane and radical processes amongst the personal and institutional networks whereby novel statistics were rapidly legitimised in the public sphere.

Negotiating Public/Private Boundaries through Minutiae: How Information Systems (De)legitimate Governmental Knowledge in Government Outsourcing *Annalisa Pelizza, Dpt Philosophy and Communication, University of Bologna*

This presentation furthers a sociomaterial framework to examine how public/private boundaries can be de facto (if not de jure) shifted throughout government IT outsourcing. By showing how public-sector IT technological efforts can be made legitimate, or on the contrary how their legitimacy can be undermined, it aims to contribute to a material understanding of how governmental IT knowledge can be (de)legitimated at the micro level of information systems adoptions, design and decisions. I argue that boundaries in outsourcing relationships can be de facto enacted through definitions of what counts as relevant knowledge. Information systems have a key role in eliciting such definitions, thus establishing knowledge asymmetries and regimes of inclusion and exclusion. I eventually show that understanding knowledge asymmetries triggered at the micro-level of information systems can help to examine macro-scale transformations between the Public and the Private, and thus seed capabilities for denationalization already inside the National. To illustrate the framework, two ethnographic case studies of governmental IT projects are discussed. The first case concerns a permit and licence submission service in Italy. The second case analyses a 20-year-long database integration carried on at the Dutch land registry. In the first case, information systems legitimated a form of knowledge developed by contractors; in the second case, the integration process valued knowledge developed in-house. I draw on these cases to argue that (de)legitimation of public-sector technoscientific endeavours is not irrecoverable, but rather depends on design and implementation choices made at the level of sociotechnical minutiae.

Session Organizers:

Janet Vertesi, Princeton University

Alondra Nelson, Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton

Chair:

danah boyd, Microsoft Research / Data & Society

246. Workshop: Collective Writing and Editing Practices of Short Pieces for 4S Backchannels Blog

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

This session brings together the transnational team of editors and assistant editors of Backchannels, the blog for all 4S news. We publish writing in the form of reflections, projects, interviews, and reports on recent conferences, meetings, and other innovative and creative gatherings. Backchannels specializes in short-form writing of up to 1,000 words in length, which is also the conventional length of most press and media. Short-form writing is a crucial means for public engagement, outreach beyond academic

audiences, and garner impacts on your research. Blog posts allow for timelier publication of research with a peer review experience. This workshop will begin with updates and insights into the past years of Backchannels' publications. You can then propose (your) future short pieces for the Backchannels blog. We will try to match with the corresponding editor (depending on schedule availability). In the second half of the workshop session, we will collectively start writing a report-back on the virtual 4S conference in Toronto. We will edit and finalize the post by the end of the meeting to publish it shortly after that. The workshop is open to everyone attending the conference. We highly encourage students and early career researchers to join us. We will provide further details and links before and during the meeting. Keep an eye on the @4sWeb Twitter account and our blog.

Session Organizer:

Olivia Doggett, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

Chair:

Yana Boeva, University of Stuttgart

247. Toxic Entanglements: acting on slow, invisible, and emerging realities - I: Systemic Entanglements

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Over the past two hundred years of industrialization, societies and scientists have struggled to keep track of the safety profiles of chemicals, both the long-used ones and the constant stream of new chemicals used in agriculture and homes and in cosmetics, supplements, and pharmaceuticals. More often than not, when chemicals appear on the market, their risk profiles are poorly understood and are used for many years before evidence of harm emerges. Knowledge of toxicities is generated by researchers working in a range of disciplines, each of which producing field-specific knowledge with their own measurement techniques, resulting in their own "agential cut" (Barad 2007). Measurements of chemical toxicities furthermore change over time. In the early twentieth century, animal studies were used to define threshold levels below which substances were deemed safe, while nowadays, it is recognized that some chemicals can disrupt endocrine systems and cause cancers even at very low levels of exposure. Overall there is very little knowledge on the effects of the multitude of chemicals that make up our every-day lives (Murphy 2008). Thus, what we know about entangled toxicities of chemicals is partial and in flux. How can we make poorly understood slow toxicities visible, and what are the challenges in doing so? We seek contributions that analyze how policymakers, researchers, artists, and activists confront these challenges, including how they seek to make the entangled toxicities visible and intervene to prevent toxicities. We invite both theoretical and methodological papers on these critical questions.

Participants:

Colonial Fallout, Chemopolitical Borders, and Monazite's Toxic Trace *Henry N Osman, Brown University*

This paper follows monazite, a radioactive mineral ore, from Shinkolobwe, a mine in the Belgian Congo, to 1127 Irving Avenue, a superfund site in Brooklyn. A side product of monazite refining is thorium oxalate, and from 1920 until 1947 the Wolff-Alport Corporation, at their factory at 1127 Irving Avenue, dumped excess radioactive thorium oxalate sludge directly into Brooklyn sewers. The landscape produced by the decades-long event of radiation exposure slowly burns, irradiating the people who continue to live and work on top of and close to the site. I argue that the radiation emanating from below produces a distinctly nuclear landscape that follows the shifting patterns of radiation beneath the ground. The nuclear relations that extend throughout the superfund site echo the colonial nuclear relations at Shinkolobwe, despite the differential effects at each site. Shinkolobwe also produced the uranium ore used in the Little Boy that flattened Hiroshima, placing domestic monazite refining in the same geo-logic as Hiroshima. Both 1127 Irving Avenue and Shinkolobwe are structured by a distinct set of relations between radioactive material and ground but share the same source. I ask what sort of territory emerges when raw

radioactive material from a colonial mine is exported and irradiates new soil across the Atlantic. Put differently: I am asking where 1127 Irving Avenue is. While legally and juridically it lies on the border of Brooklyn and Queens, the radiation at the site exceeds and leaks past those borders. I term this second chemical border the 'chemopolitical' border. By tracing monazite's supply chain, I examine the fallout of colonialism and the ways that the colony, and its toxic nuclear relations, exists inside of and below empire.

Enduring pollution and cultural revolutions in West Indian territories: rethinking nature, economy, politics and society
Jessica Oublie, Independent author

When I arrived in Guadeloupe in February 2018, I discovered that part of the land, seas, and rivers is polluted for centuries by chlordecone, an ultra-persistent pesticide used in banana plantations between 1972 and 1993. I then embarked on a painful quest to make sense of how such an ecocide was made possible. The graphic novel "Tropiques Toxiques" is the result of 136 interviews conducted in Guadeloupe, Martinique, France, Belgium and the US. It narrates how *le vivant* in our post-colonial territories - due to the persistence of the banana monoculture - is enslaved by man for economic purposes, mainly to meet consumer needs in former colonial mainland France. It questions how national and supra-national institutions "normalize" toxicity in our world through regulations that facilitate the ever-increasing presence of chemicals in daily life. It bears witness to struggles in the West Indies for a political ecology more respectful of a land already largely deprived of its nourishing capital. Through photographic portraits of fishermen, breeders, fish farmers, individuals, "Tropiques Toxiques" shows how the West Indies' culture and socialities have been impacted by pollution. Through its pages, it delves into how everyone must learn to live in contaminated territories and identifies some of the possible ways this novel experience of bearing the indelible mark of a toxic world (95% of Guadeloupeans and 92% of Martiniqueans have chlordecone in their blood) should invite us to a cultural revolution regarding our way of living on Earth to reconcile society, economy, politics and the environment.

PFAS Ubiquity as Corporate Accomplishment *Lauren Richter, Rhode Island School of Design; Grace Poudrier, Northeastern University*

While in recent years significant attention has been drawn to ubiquitous global per-and polyfluoroalkyl substances (PFAS) contamination, little scholarship has addressed the historical (and continuing) production of PFAS markets by multinational chemical corporations. This presentation reframes PFAS contamination. We shift from characterizing PFAS chemicals as "emerging contaminants" due to a state of prior ignorance about their scientific adverse effects, towards understanding their ubiquitous presence as an indicator of corporate logics, goal-oriented strategies, and markers of capitalist achievement. We examine how chemical manufacturers intentionally constructed consumer markets for PFAS in the aftermath of World War II. We argue that to more accurately theorize the structural power of multinational corporations, we need to grapple with militarism, racial capitalism, and heteropatriarchy. In the case of the production of PFAS markets, we note how the use of white, heterosexual female imagery in product advertising functioned to: a) normalize the use of synthetic military chemicals in domestic space, and b) construct Global North middle-class consumer desire. Complementing scholarship on how industries attempt to legitimate themselves post-crisis (York & Bell 2010; Benson & Kirsch 2010), we draw attention to how racialized and gendered advertising for Teflon (1950-1980) was used to hail white, female, middle-class imaginaries as a route to securing brand loyalty and ritualistic consumption at key life stages (e.g. the bridal shower). Finally, we link multi-decade chemical industry PR efforts to create markets for PFAS to the industry's current efforts to preserve and grow their markets, despite

evidence of irreversible harm and permanent global contamination.

Radioactive Entanglements: Suing the State for the Erasure of Lived Experiences *Chikako Takeshita, University of California, Riverside*

Residents living in areas around Fukushima that are affected by the nuclear meltdown in March 2011 continue to be exposed to low-dose radiation in the environment. In addition, they have most likely taken in radioactive material into their bodies through food, water, and breathing. They are entangled with radiation from the inside and outside, and for an unforeseen future when damaged cells might turn up as cancer. Toxicities of radiation at a constant low-dose and exposure from within the body are poorly understood. The Japanese government has thwarted questions about the health effects of radioactive residues by raising the acceptable dose of ambient radiation exposure by 20 times of pre-accident level and through aggressive rehabilitation of the contaminated regions. Journalists, doctors, and scientists have spoken up against the illegitimacy of the national policies to no avail. Ordinary people continue to live in the radioactive entanglement, some accepting or ignoring the risks and others resisting privately in small ways. One public attempt to challenge the semiotic erasure of radiation is the "The Right for Children to Avoid Radiation" lawsuit, which tries to hold the state accountable for protecting the rights of children to live in a safe environment and for exposing them to unnecessary levels of radiation with misleading information in the aftermath of the accident. This paper examines the plaintiff's struggle to untangle the radioactive muddle created by the state and to make the effects of radiation on ordinary citizens visible and undeniable in court.

Session Organizer:

Anita Hardon

Discussants:

Tait Mandler, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research
Elizabeth Roberts, University of Michigan

248. Plenary - Unsettling Science I

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: Auditorium

Participants:

Interdependence as a Political Technology: Crip Technosciences and Disability Justice *Aimi Hamraie, Vanderbilt University*

How do critical disability frameworks describe interdependence as a technology (e.g. a tool that extends what bodies can do) for forging political relations? Where ableism and racism intersect, where does interdependence gesture toward disability culture, even when disability results from debilitation and state violence? How do disabled people use technology to form kinships and access intimacies? How do these uses challenge foundational concepts within STS?

On Anti-Colonialism in Space *Uahikea Maile, University of Toronto*

In what ways, discursive and non-discursive, is space exploration colonial? How is space exploration produced through colonial relationships of domination, dehumanization, elimination, and dispossession? How then does space exploration reproduce these relations-on-Earth beyond it? In what ways do Indigenous criticisms of development projects in the name of space exploration unsettle technoscientific conquest and its desires for time, territory, and outer space? How does anti-colonial liberation on Earth inform the theories and practices of 'anticolonialism in outer space'? Does it not? How might anti-colonial movements be abstracted and glossed in liberal demands for 'anti-colonialism in space'? How are anthropocentric ideas about both colonial relations and anti-colonial practices

indispensable yet altogether inadequate to make sense of modern space exploration, human settlement beyond our planet and solar system, and discovery and contact with nonhuman life in the universe?

Session Organizer:

Kim Tallbear, University of Alberta

Discussants:

Shay-Akil McLean, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Aimi Hamraie, Vanderbilt University

Ahikea Maile, University of Toronto

249. Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy/Session 3: Pandemic Technologies

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

The Comparative Covid Response: Crisis, Knowledge, Policy (CompCoRe) project, comprising over sixty scholars with interdisciplinary expertise in STS, law, public policy, and the social sciences, has spent a year analyzing national policy responses to the pandemic in sixteen countries across five continents (website: compcore.cornell.edu). Our analysis shows that the pandemic is not simply a public health crisis to be managed by listening to “science” as conventional wisdom would have it. Rather, the Covid-19 crisis is playing out in unexpected and non-linear ways within the interlocking arenas of public health, economy, and politics against a continually shifting terrain of scientific, socioeconomic, and political developments. Our research identifies patterned responses across countries that demonstrate how the pandemic found and exacerbated underlying structural weaknesses in national response systems, and it highlights the need for reforms in current institutional approaches to preparedness in global health crises. Countries represented in CompCoRe include Australia, Austria, Brazil, China, France, Germany, India, Indonesia, Italy, Japan, the Netherlands, Peru, Singapore, South Korea, Sweden, Taiwan, the United Kingdom, and the United States. The panel will feature comparative analyses of national efforts to enroll reliable epidemiological and biomedical expertise, resolve difficult trade-offs, manage the economic fallout of the pandemic, and build political support for effective implementation, among other topics. We aim to open up new questions about public health sovereignty, crisis management, and global flows of knowledge and power among experts, states, and citizens. You can learn more about CompCoRe at compcore.cornell.edu.

Participants:

Covid-19, the GHSI, and the Global Health Imaginary. *Jeremy Baskin*, *The University of Melbourne*

In October 2019, shortly before the Covid-19 pandemic erupted, the Global Health Security Index (GHSI) was released. It was the product of an eminent group of experts, involving Johns Hopkins University and the Open Philanthropy Project (comprising the Bill and Melinda Gates Foundation among others). It purported to assess and rank pandemic preparedness, country by country, against a universal set of metrics. The US was ranked ‘most prepared’ followed by the UK, whilst Vietnam came in 50th position just ahead of China, and Cuba could be found near the bottom of the rankings. Mere months later, as Covid-19 spread worldwide, it became apparent that this GHSI assessment was almost totally contradicted by the “facts on the ground”. Global Health comprises an assemblage of institutions and experts (WHO, Gates Foundation, Covax and so on), a set of views and imaginaries regarding what public health is and should be, and organising mechanisms through which the health relations and health priorities, and research and funding flows, between global North and South are measured and managed. Arguably, Global Health has been everywhere and nowhere during the coronavirus pandemic. Using the example of the GHSI I examine how the imaginaries and practices of Global Health security shaped the index, and privileged particular values, behaviours and norms of conduct. I ask why the experts who produced the GHSI got things so wrong. I suggest that the role of philanthro-capitalists

and the directionality of flows of pandemic knowledge between North and South needs to be rethought.

Big Data" as a Metaphor? Digital Technologies and Taiwan's Covid-19 Responses. *Shun-Ling Chen*, *Institutum Jurisprudentiae, Academia Sinica*; *Yuling Huang*, *National Cheng Kung University*

At a moment when science and technologies are called to rescue the global society from the pandemic, a careful examination on how they are employed and at what cost is crucial. In this paper, we focus on Taiwan government's use of digital technologies as part of its responses to the Covid-19 outbreak, including allowing public health authorities to link various public and private databases for border control, quarantine enforcement and contact tracing. The government has emphasized its employment of digital technologies, and touted the use of "big data" as instrumental for its ability to keep the virus under control. Nevertheless, the actual efficacy of digital technologies remains an open question, and the unprecedented use of personal data has raised privacy concerns. As Taiwan is known to have successfully prevented the spread of Covid-19 within its border, and as the Taiwan government is eager to export its model as a digital democracy, its strategies and tools have the potential to influence policymakers in other countries. After an overview of the digital technologies in Taiwan's Covid-19 responses, we discuss the understanding and assessment of such deployment by investigating three types of speakers: government officials, the media, and peer-review scientific papers. We take into account the target audience of these speakers, which may vary from the local public to the international community. We discuss the concerns, as well as the cost, overt and hidden, of the (potentially) overhyped technological solution for the prolonged pandemic.

Testing Testing: How the United States's Preoccupation with Covid-19 Testing Undermined the Pandemic Management. *Onur Ozgode*, *Harvard STS Program, Harvard Kennedy School*

Covid on Campus: Social Control and Solidarity in Universities' Pandemic Responses *Margarita Rayzberg*, *Cornell University STS*

Session Organizers:

Sheila Jasanoff, Harvard University

Stephen Hilgartner, Department of Science & Technology Studies/ Cornell University

Ben Hurlbut, Arizona State University

Onur Ozgode, Harvard STS Program, Harvard Kennedy School

Margarita Rayzberg, Cornell University STS

250. Decolonizing the Canon - Part II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Participants:

Analyzing documents in and with STS: A practice-oriented method *Hilde Reinertsen*, *The TIK-centre, University of Oslo*; *Kristin Asdal*, *TIK, Centre for Technology, Innovation and Culture*

In STS, ethnographic accounts of science-in-the-making and politics-by-other-means has long held the status as the method of choice for grasping practices as they unfold, both in the lab and in the wild. Yet, as rewarding as this has been, it has also served to eclipse other scholarly traditions, notably the text- and history-oriented humanities. It has also eclipsed other important matters of concern, notably how documents are often key to how practices unfold, issues come into being and governing happens. This paper proposes to reposition these methodological and empirical matters of concern at the heart of STS. Indeed, STS approaches used to be informed by texts and semiotics, as seen in

the vibrant tradition of material semiotics and conceptual tools such as Shapin&Schaffer's 'textual technologies' and Latour&Woolgar's 'inscription devices' (Asdal&Jordheim 2018). In revisiting these original contributions and recombining them with the text-oriented humanities and the practice-oriented methods in STS, we put forward a method that we label 'practice-oriented document analysis' (Asdal 2015, Asdal&Reinertsen 2020, forthcoming 2021). In doing this, the paper presents six 'methodological moves' that enable us to better analyse documents in and as practice: 'document-as-site', 'document-as-tool', 'document-work', 'document-as-text', 'document-issues' and 'document-movements'.

Intentional Assemblies in Times and Places *Chun-Yu (Jo Ann) Wang, Stanford University; Eduard Leonard Fanthome, Stanford Anthropology Dept*

Latourian Actor-Network-Theory (ANT) and its reconceptualization of the "social" and the "political" has become influential and canonized in STS and related disciplines since the 1980s. In his polemical essay "When ANT meets SPIDER," British social anthropologist Ingold challenges some fundamental formulations of ANT by questioning the nature of social relations, the condition for connection, the location of agency, and the principle of symmetry (Ingold 2008). Similarly, archaeologists like Bauer and Kosiba have reframed the agency of things and people as an emergent potential within politically inflected contingent associations of people organisms and things, conditioned by materials and human values. Building on but not limited to the abovementioned critical engagements with ANT, our presentation seeks to explore and further three analytics from the perspectives of anthropology and archaeology. The first analytic engages with ANT's notion of "space." We examine the spatial assumptions which underlie Latour's theorizations of networks and emphasize the need to attend to differentially spatialized, territorialized, materialized, and practiced connectivity. The second analytic engages with ANT's notion of "time." We examine the synchronous tendencies entailed in Latour's anti-structure theoretical position and suggest how we might account for the enduring, sedimented cultural-historical structural patterns and power relations without compromising our sensitivity to the "contingent" and the "emergent." The third and last analytic engages with ANT's notion of "agency." We argue that a practice theory-oriented analysis is useful in thinking about the questions of action, intentionality, subjectivity, and responsibility and show how ethnographic and archaeological methods might be uniquely positioned to make contributions to this conversation. We hope that our presentation will bring critical anthropological and archeological insights into Latourian ANT and demonstrate their potential to address questions of agency, spatiality and temporality it raises.

Map, Campaign, or Participate: Pluriversal Methodology in STS Research *Thomas Rickard, Instituto de Geociências (IGC), Universidade Federal Minas Gerais (UFMG)*
Studies conducted today by or in collaboration with Western and/or privileged researchers encounter a multifaceted paradoxical position related to institutional orientation and methodology. On the one hand, science-production is tied to governance that represents the continuation of centuries of brutal, extractivist colonialism. On the other, for the institutions in which we are often embedded, efficient, consensual and sustainable environmental sciences and governance can rescue the future, holding open the possibility of both producing power inequities and reliably distinguishing real threats to egalitarian social objectives. Further, even as academic norms demand quantitative evidence and transparent sources and modes of analysis, apolitical researcher and methodology as a neutral tool to reveal reality is incoherent, itself distinctly Modern. Yet beginning the research process with inflexible, if well founded, assumptions about capitalism and technoscience risks failing to see what is beyond these categories. This is a contribution to

debate on practices within STS and related fields from authors such as Marilyn Strathern, Helen Verran, Sandra Harding, John Law, Donna Haraway, to hold the tension without resolution – to build research, including methods, with participants for shared or divergent and compatible aims; to name political values, but explain how these are explicitly embedded from design to implementation; to help build decolonial worlds, including with scientific tools and collaborative intervention propositions. As such, methodology becomes a contingent and evolving attempt to state position and orientation, a politically and scientifically accountable claim to good relations with humans and more-than-humans. The researcher does not map, or campaign, but participate.

Torqued Typologies: Rethinking Systems of Classification Through the Critical Potential of Latinx Studies *Javier Rivera, Annenberg School for Communication & Journalism, University of Southern California*

In a recent study by Mora et al. (2021), the use of the term "Latinx" was surveyed to evaluate its adoption by Latinxs across varying political ideologies, immigrant generation, and birth cohort. In their survey construction, the use of and identification with the gender-neutral panethnic label was measured with the categories: "not at all," "rarely," "sometimes," and "very often." In an effort to capture the practice of self-identification with a panethnic label, respondents were made to reflect through a scale of time. What does it mean to measure, categorize, and classify Latinidad through this and other logics of stability and precision? With the former and other cases in mind, this paper explores the ways the field of science and technology studies has conceptualized the practices of measuring, categorizing, and classifying and the socio-material work they do to the Latinx typologies that result. The normative claims made by moments of classification are considered through the tension, or torque (Bowker and Star, 1999), created where competing systems of classification meet. To address the dynamics of non-scalability and incommensurability Latinx theories of border subjectivity (Viego, 2007), the brown commons (Muñoz, 2020), and colonial time (Ruiz, 2019) will be used to consider the ways STS artifacts of study such as scale, infrastructure, automation, and algorithmic systems can be re-thought when evaluating the creation of Latinx typologies.

Session Organizer:

Tiên-Dung Hà, Stanford University

Discussant:

SY Cheung

251. Radical Care in Feminist Digital Spaces II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

The increasing digitalization of everyday life reveals a growing activity/presence of feminist practices in the digital sphere (D'Ignazio and Klein 2020; Jarvis 2009; McLean 2020). Such practices reconfigure the digital space and generate more safe, just, inclusive and unoppressive places (Young 1986) that challenge sexist and exclusionary practices. Moreover, in the recent/ongoing pandemic crisis where the digital sphere has augmented, (digital) care practices have gained a distinctive and leading role in people's everyday lives. Standing against the neoliberal tradition of individualism and commodification, 'radical care is often connected to positive political change by providing spaces of hope in dark times' (Hobart and Kneese, 2020: x). In a world overwhelmed by systemic sexism and multiple crises of care, crises of care, such emancipatory possibilities of digital space are bound to play a central role. This panel shifts attention towards feminist practices of radical care in the digital space and explores their genealogies, characteristics, dynamics, and limitations. We welcome contributions using transdisciplinary and intersectional methods to discuss digital care as related with understandings of inclusion, solidarity and interdependence. How can we theorize a more expanded notion, language and practice of care in the digital space? What

would an understanding of radical care mean in relation with data management, digital security and infrastructure? How can radical practices challenge institutional carelessness and 'carewashing'? How are existing platforms (re)shaped in more inclusive ways through intersectional practices of care? How does an STS perspective trouble notions of radical care, feminism and digital space? How can STS research on radical care and feminist digital practices reinforce and promote feminist knowledge production?

Participants:

Enacting the Affective Body: Contraceptive Self-tracking as a Feminist Practice *Ellen Algera, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research, University of Amsterdam*

Hundreds of fertility-tracking applications (apps) have been launched over the past decades. Current research on reproductive self-tracking critically argues that reproductive tracking apps lead to the disciplining and the self-alienation of users, as the hierarchical opposition between objective numerical data and lived and embodied experiences is reinforced (Kressbach, 2019; Lupton, 2015, 2016; Novotny & Hutchinson, 2019). In this presentation, I use a feminist material semiotic approach to move beyond an analysis of reproductive self-tracking that is centred around the disciplining effects of these technologies. Instead, I focus on how everyday reproductive self-tracking is productive of both knowledge of the body and practices of embodiment. Based on ethnographic fieldwork with users residing in the Netherlands, I will detail how the reproductive body is enacted in the everyday knowledge practices of users of apps who prevent pregnancy. In these practices, users attempt to disrupt the salient ways in which (reproductive) bodies are known, stigmatised, disciplined and medicalised. By collecting data and cultivating awareness of their (reproductive) bodies, users trace the ways in which their body is involved in and affected by systems (of power, discourse, hormones) and imagine new ways of doing, scripting and relating to the body. By engaging in the affective practices of cultivating awareness of and "embracing" their body, users both attempt to disrupt salient norms, while at the same time producing new ones. Particularly in the ideal of the "natural body" - a body that is not intervened in medically - is evoked frequently - masking the complex everyday negotiations with which users enact this "natural body".

Mobile apps for the illiterate from their cultural perception of ICT Self-learning among the Yoruba people in Benin Republic *Aimé Dafon Sègla, Université d'Abomey-Calavi*

Abstract Mobile phones and web digital tools contribute to the personal development. It also allows capacity to develop initiatives for economic growth. Yet, many people cannot benefit from the new technologies because mobile phones and web infrastructures in sub-Saharan Africa are configured in foreign languages that people - non-literate in - don't write and understand. Furthermore, basic functions such as text messaging, internet web 2.0, e-commerce, media, and web communication are underutilized (Sègla 2019). Thus, only the 'call' function is used. Obviously, the solution seems to be the manufacturing or adaptation of phones in the language of the local (Sègla 2016, 2014, 2003). In this paper, I criticize the exclusion of illiterate indigenous populations from access to ICT. Illiteracy and language barriers remain indeed a major challenge for digitalization in Africa. SMS, online platforms - e.government or social media - rely only on written words and are not designed in local dialects. Thus, Yoruba illiterates struggle with the use of Information Communication Technology (ICT), being unable to even buy airtimes - credit - for the phone or know their own mobile phone numbers. However, even in these conditions of under-utilization and handicap, local people are innovative by creating new procedural knowledge. People work around issues by appropriating ICT to suit their needs. In Central Benin Republic, illiterates develop alternative strategies, signs, images, specific symbols, and voice messages on whatsapp to benefit

from ICT. The study is a report of these local inventions. It is based on interviews with approximately forty people who are primarily female and male traders or peasants, art craft, or members of convents. The ethnographic research has focused on the local perceptions of ICT and on knowledge production contextual concepts based for adaptation. Starting from these on-site creations, mobile application software - mobile apps - that is capable of contributing additional value and facilitating local people's training and education is envisaged. Mobile app "Je M'EDUQUE" is intended to adapt ICT but also to help reading and write in the mother tongue. This is illustrated by exploring Vygotsky (1983) approaches revisiting Piaget (2008). In conclusion, the project will facilitate the development of indigenous languages as a basis for diffusing science for development and new technologies, as well as for innovation and for more ethical and inclusive economic development of the African society south of the Sahara. Keywords: Africanizing ICT; mother tongue; education and training; knowledge production; epistemology: culture-technology-innovation; concept: history-culture-logic. References: Piaget J., *Psychologie et pédagogie, folio essais*, 2008 Sègla D. A., « Images and Voices from Digital Africa - Part II », Ta-Tup, Special Issue on Digitalization in the Global South, University of Tübingen, Germany, 2019. Sègla D. A. « La force agissante du mot, de la phrase-mot et des métaphores Yoruba dans la formation du vocabulaire scientifique: le développement de la langue comme la condition de la possibilité conceptuelle », *Cahier d'Etudes Linguistiques N°11, Université d'Abomey-Calavi*, pp. 109-143, 2016. Sègla D. A. « Eléments de Prospective d'anthropologie expérimentale de l'introduction de la langue maternelle dans l'enseignement de la science et de la technologie en République du Bénin », *Cahiers d'Etudes Linguistiques, Revue du Département des Sciences du Langage et de la Communication, Université d'Abomey-Calavi*, 8:214-257, 2014. Sègla D. A. « The Scientific Mind and Cultural Articulation in an Oral Society: language as a mirror », *Social Science Information, SAGE Publications (London, Thousand Oaks, CA and New Delhi)*, 42(3): 339-374, 2003. Vygotsky, S., « Le problème de l'enseignement et du développement mental à l'âge scolaire. » In J.P. Bronckart et J.V. Wertsch (dir.), *Vygotsky aujourd'hui* (p. 95-117). Neuchâtel : Delachaux et Niestlé, 1983.

#allowyourself: young Brazilian Black women and self-care in online spaces of sociability *Julia de Souza Abdalla, Universidade Estadual de Campinas - Unicamp; Ana Cesaltina Marques, Universidade Federal do Ceará*

Spaces of sociability in websites and social media currently enable Black women to produce counternarratives that unsettle stereotypes limiting subjective expression. Being strong, resistant to pain, and labeled a warrior are not just possibilities, but expectations with which Black women are culturally and socially pushed to comply. In Brazil, such traits relate to their historically assigned social roles traceable back to the country's roots in slavery. Young Black activists' recent engagement with image and textual expressions in social media has resulted in the creation of conversational spaces where new ways of dealing with the drawbacks of daily life and self-care practices are produced along with a plurality of dispositions and affections and shared with their followers. Such procedures are understood as one of the contemporary and generational expressions of Brazilian Black feminism, which has recently sought social networks to disseminate its main issues and produce identity shifts in a performative fashion. This work analyzes a selection of narratives published on Instagram, grouped by hashtags that refer to Black women's practices of self-care. It applies critical discourse analysis as a theoretical frame, understanding texts as linguistic-discursive practices intertwined with social, political, historical, and cultural structures. Discursive enunciation is thus understood as a form of action that both produces and transforms subjectivities. The analysis is organized around the following

questions: which practices of self-care are most frequently referenced by Brazilian Black women? Can the production of “self-narratives” be considered a form of self-care? keywords: self-narratives; self-care; Black women; social media; Brazil.

Session Organizer:

Vasiliki Makrygianni

Chair:

Hara Kouki, University of Crete

252. Composting Feminisms and Environmental Humanities

Panel - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Composting, as a feminist practice, has been taken up by an open, cross-institutional, trans-disciplinary reading and research group exploring the traces, legacies and relations between inclusive feminisms and broad Environmental Humanities over the last six years. The Composting Feminisms and Environmental Humanities group wishes to connect with composting kin around the world through this second open panel at 4S. At 4S 2018 we held a full day of interconnecting open discussions examining the transnational intersections between new environmentalisms and feminist STS. Forming good relations and worlding better worlds informs all of our endeavors, making 4S 2021 an ideal venue for Composting. The Composting group exists because although we cannot envision feminisms without attending to queer, Indigenous, anti-racist, anticolonial, crip, and other intersectional perspectives, often environmental thought neglects these questions. How might we attune ourselves to the ways in which new ideas are indebted to writings, readings and practices that have come before? How are feminist genealogies composted in and through the Environmental Humanities? What ethics of care and responsibility emerge from these ideas? What is yet to be added to the compost pile? We encourage submissions that continue the process of breaking down matters to re-emerge as new matters. Together we attune ourselves to the good (and fraught) relations that already exist and are yet to be formed between these modes of knowing. To expand the conversation, submissions that queer the traditional format and offer creative provocations which embody the research are encouraged, including performances, ficto-criticism, art and speculative design.

Participants:

Compost to Compostables: Now, What Other Figurations?

Mathew Arthur, Simon Fraser University; Reuben Jentink, Simon Fraser University

In “Composting Settler Nationalisms” (2017) we figured compost as a way of thinking about multispecies relations, implicatedness, and responsibility as non-Indigenous theorists working and writing on Indigenous territories. We made connections between colonial agricultural histories, the regenerative ontologies and operations of composting, and feminist STS material semiotics. Compost, we argued, cannot be thought separately from the habits and cultural codings of waste and recycling—urban and industrial practices enmeshed firmly in histories of nation-building and liberal ecological sensibilities. Now, in the midst of pandemic, we find ourselves surrounded by compostables: bioplastic cups and takeaway trays, markers of our sustained waste-making habits, stamped with recycling logos. In this paper, we wonder what other figurations might be put in kinship with compost, acknowledging that, as a method, compost has its risks: its political grammar of culpable posthumanism can become amenable to colonial and capitalist logics. Thinking with compost and its industrialization can sensitize us to the hazards of our methods, however angled at multispecies justice, being conscripted into institutionalizing circulations. This work extends our theorization of compost as a form of citationality: how knowledge practices are recomposed or decay in the specificities of a constituent mix, how sites of regeneration and failure trouble notions of authorship and attribution. So, like Haraway, we are keen to craft a motley kinship of accompanying figures that might work in, with, and through compost—to further enrich and

complexify the soil of STS multispecies thinking, to open generative inroads to non-institutional forms of STS literacy, and to remain responsive to the shifting attachments and desires that surround the compost pile.

Radical Composting: Cultivating Soil Kinship in Cities

Alexandra R. Toland, Bauhaus Universität Weimar;

Margarita Cristina Garcia, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar

The FAO (2015) has warned that over a third of the world’s soil resources are already “moderately to highly degraded through erosion, salinization, compaction, acidification, chemical pollution and nutrient depletion” based on human activity. This resource-centric diagnosis of the status of the world’s soils is an example of what Maria Puig de la Bellacasa (2015) refers to as “technoscientific hegemony”, driven by dominant ideals of productivity, a linear, “progressivist” understanding of innovation, and a restless futurity that envisions soil management as the best and perhaps only solution. Based on concepts of multispecies kinship (e.g. Haraway, 2016, Kirksey 2014), geontological agency (e.g. Yusoff, 2015 and Povinelli, 2016) and geological conviviality (see Reinert, 2016 and Bubandt, 2017), we explore soils as autonomous, subjective beings in multispecies communities that demand an investment of attention and time (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2015) in urban design: Soilkin. We look at three case studies of radical composting in cities to explore how different spatial and social settings influence the relationships between human and more than human populations: 1) Urbaniahoeve’s urban food forest in the Amsterdam Bijlmer; 2) Common Ground’s Prinzessinnengarten-Kreuzberg at the busy traffic circle Moritzplatz Berlin; and 3) Social Ecologies’ Soil Center on the west side of Chicago. All three projects are spearheaded by (queer)feminist artists as community organisers, radical permaculturists and compost activists, who emphasize the need for creative care, hands-on expertise, and transdisciplinary collaboration in the formation of new representations of Soilkin-friendly cities.

From the Ashes: Interrogating Systems Using Art Made from

the Remains of the Australian Bushfires Catherine Sarah Young, UNSW Sydney Art & Design

This presentation illustrates the use of ashes in art with two projects. Ash is what mostly remains after bushfire, turning formerly lush and diverse landscapes into stark and homogeneous ones. In “The Weighing of the Heart”, human heart sculptures are cast out of ashes and other organic remains from the Australian bushfires. It references the scene of the “Weighing of the Heart”, a spell in the Egyptian Book of the Dead. In casting the ashes with resin, the artist arrests metabolism of the remains back into the soil, creating objects of memory in a political landscape that forgets the bushfire crisis periodically. In “Burned Lines”, extracts from climate change denier tweets and press written to or about the artist are rewritten with ink made from the same ashes. This series explores the power we bring to words and how appropriating these to examine the role of misinformation and hate can potentially make these words lose their intended meaning. Furthermore, the project investigates the use of ash as a way to bring a sense of poetry and irony to discussing difficult issues of misinformation, post-truth, hate, and misogyny. These projects use the matter left from environmental catastrophe as a tool for conversation about climate change in the field of environmental humanities. An option is to also provide an online writing workshop where participants are invited to create their own ink made from ash.

Composting, Metabolism, After Eating *Lindsay Kelley, UNSW Art & Design*

This paper presents material from my forthcoming book, *After Eating: Metabolizing the Arts*. At the intersection of feminist theory, environmental humanities, and contemporary art practices, the stomach and digestive processes (fermentation, evacuation, the gut) emerge as central sites for theorizing the

contemporary moment, whether through pharmaceuticals, cultural and infrastructural flows, or histories of science, politics, and their overlaps. With its roots in the Greek μεταβολή (change) and βάλειν (throw), “metabolism” implies movement, unfolding, casting, and releasing. Metabolism spills beyond bodily interiors as artists and art theorists increasingly appreciate metabolism’s conceptual relevance to their work. This paper presents three projects I write about in the book, and promotes a non-invasive method inspired by the ambulatory and foraging movements that characterize scatology studies. Mary Maggic’s *Egrogen Farms* (2015) investigates kinship between women and chickens by critiquing fertility diet discourse. Ai Hasegawa’s speculative design projects *I Wanna Deliver a Dolphin* (2013) and *I Wanna Deliver a Shark* (2012) propose gestating and birthing endangered species to address both habitat loss and ticking biological clocks. Rachel Herrick’s *Museum for Obeast Conservation Studies (MOCS)* (2012-2014) turns the visual culture of “Teddy Bear Patriarchy” (Haraway) inside out to critique relationships between fat bodies and natural history. All of these projects address new understandings of links between metabolism, environment, and reproduction, what Hannah Landecker calls “fraying categories” (2013). Annemarie Mol’s *Eating in Theory* (2021) will also animate this analysis, as will her previous work about eaters as semi-permeable and not in muscular control of their digestion.

Session Organizer:

Lindsay Kelley, UNSW Art & Design

Chair:

Jennifer Mae Hamilton, University of New England

253. Doing and Making Times IV: Temporal Ontologies

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Participants:

Making Time: Techniques of Forgetting Amidst Technologies of Remembering *Elliott Hauser, The University of Texas at Austin*

Information systems are often consulted to answer questions and guide action. Information systems are generally held to track or represent some state of the world, like an inventory does. What would it mean, however, if systems did not track some state of the world but instead created it? In the terminology of propositional logic, what does it mean that some information systems contain facts instead of propositions? This paper examines the production of facts about the current time within the assemblage of computational timekeeping. From atomic clocks, through scientific time standards and network synchronization protocols to the time displayed upon smartphones, layers of certainty chain upon each other in complex ways. The many interlinked systems and practices which constitute modern computational timekeeping form an information infrastructure (Bowker et al., 2010), defined as “pervasive enabling resources in network form” (p. 98). As an infrastructure, computational timekeeping is distributed, taken for granted (Star & Ruhleder, 1996), and maintained by ‘invisible’ labor (Star, 1991). This paper analyzes this infrastructure’s role in creating the fact of the time of day, a globally ubiquitous component of what philosopher John Searle has called social reality (Searle, 2010). Specific components of the assemblage are examined recursively, including the UTC time standard, Network Time Protocol (NTP), and the tz time zone database (see Hauser, 2018). The analysis reveals contrasting examples of Bowker has called memory practices (Bowker, 2006), and which I examine as techniques of forgetting surrounding technologies of remembering.

To Be Done with the Presumption of Time’s Agency *Lee Nelson*

While the recognition of other-than-human agency has been a

bedrock of many methodological and conceptual developments of STS, this talk proposes that time’s agency, long presumed, should be revoked and denied. By ‘opening up’ the historical roots of time’s agency and finding it unnecessary, attention shifts to the material happenings that would otherwise remain shrouded by mere temporal change. Methodologically, depriving time of agency helps scholars remain attuned to material agency and occurrences. In so doing, time, or change more broadly construed, is reconfigured as a resultant, a product, rather than as a ghostly ingredient or a priori psychological, ontological, or metaphysical necessity. To support this position, this talk will examine the origin of time’s presumptive agency through attention to ex nihilo creation stories which treat time as an additive to spatial or material precursors. This bifurcated presumption and its effects have continued as a subterranean but dominant commitment within Western thought. Next, I will survey STS and adjacent scholarship that has suggested, but not committed to, the material production of time. Lastly, I will provide an exposé of my research on forensic entomologists who derive temporality from an analysis of insect behavior to provide an estimation for how long a decomposing human body has been dead. This example will function as an example of a contemporary human-nonhuman epistemic practice that denies temporal agency, how this denial methodologically directs attention to materiality, and how doing so results in time being understood as a product of said material occurrences.

Patenting the Possible, Accumulating the Intangible *Oscar Kruger, Lund University; Alexander Paulsson, Swedish National Road and Transport Research Institute*

Following an increasingly prominent ambition to substitute renewable (biological) materials for non-renewable (fossil, etc) ones, the vision of a sustainable “bioeconomy” has gained a place of prominence in the R&I policy of the EU (and beyond). Existing research has noted an existing bifurcation between two contending visions of the bioeconomy: A dominant innovation- and profit-oriented vision of high-tech entrepreneurship, as opposed a subaltern agro-ecological vision. Little research, however, has inquired into the temporal dimension that underwrites this bifurcation. In this paper, we empirically scrutinize the recent efforts a number of European bioeconomy-entrepreneurs go through in order to capture value in the form of patented control of immaterial property, and attends to the institutional and material processes that construct and maintain “intangibility” as a category. We argue that this intangibility must be understood in respect to its distinct temporal structure, where value is made to reside in promise and future possibility, and is captured by a legal framework which binds this future to an instant and actor in its own past. We conclude that the unequal prominence of the contending visions of the bioeconomy must be considered in light of their different relations to the tangible and the intangible, and to the temporal horizons that define these categories.

Session Organizer:

Filip Vostal, Institute of Philosophy of the Czech Academy of Sciences

Chair:

Helge Jordheim, University of Oslo

254. Practices of Justice, Ethics, and Participatory Research

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

This panel stages a conversation between papers that take up the the “how” of justice, ethics and participatory research. How have particular projects, policies, and fields assembled key practices that are now pervasively part of non-profit, feminist, equity-based, African American, and social justice oriented research. What exactly is meant by justice in different domains of research? When designers put “ethics first” what does that mean? Who gets credit for innovations in research practice and how are these cited?

How have innovations in participatory research been created and credited between academic researchers and non-profit equity-based community work? This panel thickens are understanding of these key terms of "good relations" in research.

Participants:

Ethics and values in design: a structured review and theoretical critique *Joseph Donia, University of Toronto; James Shaw, Women's College Hospital*

A variety of approaches have appeared in academic literature and in design practice representing "ethics-first" methods. These approaches typically focus on clarifying the normative dimensions of design, or outlining strategies for explicitly incorporating values into design. While this body of literature has developed considerably over the last 20 years, two themes central to the endeavour of ethics and values in design (E+VID) have yet to be discussed in relation to each other: (a) designer agency, and (b) the strength of normative claims informing the design process. To address this gap, this paper presents a structured review of leading E+VID approaches and critiques, and classifies them according to their positions on normative strength, and views regarding designer agency. Seventeen distinct approaches and 12 critiques that met inclusion criteria for our review were identified. Included papers were distributed across the spectrum of views regarding normative strength, and we found that no approaches and only one critique that represented a view characteristic of "low" designer agency. We suggest that the absence of "low" designer agency approaches results in the neglect of crucial influences on design as targets of intervention by designers. We conclude with suggestions for future research that might illuminate strategies to achieve ethical design in information mature societies, and argue that without attending to the tensions raised by balancing normatively "strong" visions of the future, with limitations imposed on designer agency in corporate-driven design settings, "meaningful" ethical design will continue to encounter challenges in practice.

Impact of Loretta Jones on Community-Partnered Participatory Research Utilizing the h-index and Other Publication Metrics *Shari Randolph, University of California Los Angeles (UCLA); Darlene Parker-Kelly, Charles R. Drew University; Felicia Jones, Healthy African American Families; Andrea Jones; Gilbert Ramirez, Texas A&M University; Thomas Belin, UCLA*

Pioneering contributions to social justice made by self-made community scientist Dr. Loretta Jones, through her leadership of the Los Angeles-based non-profit organization Healthy African American Families II (HAAF), a standard-bearer for "Community Partnered Participatory Research" (CPPR), a refinement of community-based participatory research emphasizing principles of engagement that could sustain the impact of research findings. Among other reflections of her impact, we were interested to utilize the h-index (Hirsh, 2005) and other publication metrics to characterize the relevance and impact. As explained in Jones (2018), Dr. Jones coined the term CPPR with Keith Norris, MD, PhD in 1992, growing out of discussions of how communities and academia could collaborate as true partners in research and community capacity building to address disparities in health while building community resilience. CPPR began with a focus on preterm birth and grew to encompass many other aspects of health. The framework blossomed and matured through its rigorous implementation in the context of mental health research carried out with the benefit of energized community engagement, notably through collaborative efforts to address depression in partnership with Ken Wells, MD, MPH (Jones, 2018). Their jointly authored article on CPPR principles in the *Journal of the American Medical Association* (Jones and Wells 2007) is a landmark in the field that has been cited over 500 times, while the h-index associated with her publications reflects the substantial breadth

of her research impact. The presentation will review the ongoing impact of Dr. Jones through publication metrics that complement recognitions of her work.

Inquiries into the standard of justice in biomedicine: The general, the specific, and the procedural *Yoshio Nakaga, Sophia University*

In recent years, scholars in science and technology studies have advanced an explanatory analysis of justice in scientific work and regulations. Despite the findings of local justice, only a few studies have probed what concept of justice a group of individuals use in biomedicine and how the principle of justice and its rule of subject selection, the equitable procedure of selecting participants in research, have been created by bioethics commissions and federal agencies, and enforced by institutional review boards (IRBs). This paper argues that the understanding of justice in biomedicine requires an investigation into the standard of justice that consists of its principles and rules of subject selection. Methodology here employs historical case studies of biomedical and government institutions in the United States. My analysis demonstrates that the coordination of these tangible criteria has generated what bioethicists call a "paradigm shift," or innovation in review mechanisms, thus developing justice as balancing during the 1990s. This change has simultaneously involved the separation and balance of three institutions: bioethics commissions provide the general design of the standards of justice; federal agencies transmute the disparate measures of justice into a specific hybrid rule; and IRBs offer procedures for translating these standards to rule-enactment.

Session Organizer:

Yoshio Nakaga, Sophia University

255. Living with Computing: Postphenomenological Studies

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Contemporary digital technologies are transforming everything from the ways we engage in political discussion, to the ways we wear our clothing, to the ways we exist in city spaces, to the ways we find love. In this panel we explore all of these topics, and draw out their implications through the use of ideas from the postphenomenological school of thought. With its focus on technological materiality and human-technology relations, notions from postphenomenology prove useful for analyzing and critiquing the ways that digital technologies shape so many aspects of modern life. In our first paper, Olya Kudina and Bas de Boer explore the possible effects of cutting-edge AI on the issue of online political rhetoric, with implications for everything from chatbot design to online journalism. Nicola Liberati uses postphenomenology to investigate the ways smart textiles mediate human relationships and emotions, exploring their role in techno-imaginaries in China. Our third paper takes a look at the aesthetics of the city, as Sanna Lehtinen & Delfina Fantini van Ditmar consider how emerging 5G connectivity is reshaping urban life and politics. And Ciano Aydin brings in Lacanian psychoanalysis to explore the ways persuasive technologies influence our behaviors, with a detour through the case of the Tinder dating app.

Participants:

GPT-3 and the Technological Mediation of Political Language *Olga Kudina, University of Twente (the Netherlands); Bas de Boer, University of Twente (the Netherlands)*

GPT-3 is often presented as a breakthrough in AI, because of its ability to write convincing texts in different styles when presented with an opening sentence and thereby fasten and improve the writing of legal briefs, help forming more consumer-friendly chatbots, write creative and journalistic texts and ease the process of text comprehension. Critics have downplayed the optimism around GPT-3 by suggesting that there are still many flaws in its design, making its capacity of reasoning far inferior to what humans are capable of. Regardless of whether GPT-3 can be attributed with consciousness, it remains a powerful technology that can be used as a faster vehicle to write, read, and

disseminate texts. In this presentation, we explore the political consequences of these possibilities. As a starting-point, we suggest that GPT-3 fuels the functionalization of language, and explore the consequences of this functionalization in the context of journalism, as well as the dissemination of not fact-checked information on digital media. Drawing from technological mediation theory, we explore how both writers and readers of texts are constituted as political subjects in their interactions with GPT-3. We do so by discussing GPT-3 in relation to the theories of politics developed by Hannah Arendt and Michel Foucault. Building on those thinkers, we suggest that the wide-spread use of GPT-3 forces us to think about how “spaces of deliberation” can still be constructed through exercising “counter-conduct” against the functionalization of language.

5G Aesthetics: Hidden in Plain Sight *Sanna Lehtinen, Aalto University; Delfina Fantini van Ditmar, Royal College of Art*

As we move further into the 21st-century hyper-connectivity paradigm, different types of cities' aesthetic identity are changing unforeseeably due to new technological advancement. By enabling faster and more steady connections, the fifth generation of mobile internet connectivity '5G', offers a new platform for large-scale adoption of technologies including self-driving vehicles (SDVs) developments. Being faster than 4G requires a greater density of small cells towers installations, leading to modified landscapes. Cities colonised by numerous antennas result in a quick aesthetic push raising concerns of strongly altered environments. Marketers and councils are promoting the upgrade to a faster service. Yet, the unplanned effects for entire cityscapes have not been fully revealed nor discussed so far. As such, 5G is forming into an increasingly central component of contemporary technological mediation of urban aesthetic experiences. The aesthetic and experiential effects of 5G are already cause of a critical urban debate. This paper presents a joint perspective combining philosophical urban aesthetics with design research methodology to uncover socio-political issues and how the ongoing shift in technology affects the look and feel of cities worldwide.

Technology, Desire and Tinder *Ciano Aydin, University of Twente (the Netherlands)*

The influence of technology on behavior is extensively studied in all kinds of contexts, both within and outside academia. In the development of new technologies, more and more attention is being paid to how behaviour is and can be changed with technology and under which (political, ethical) conditions this is justified. The debate on persuasive technology is perhaps the strongest illustration of this. However, there is little attention for the influence of technology on a less visible dimension of humans, which is nevertheless of eminent importance for the way in which technology influences them, including their behaviour, namely desire. In this paper, I examine how technology influences desire. An analysis of the structure of desire will contribute to understanding how people are formed and even shaped by technology. In the analysis of desire, inspiration will be found in the thinking of the French psychoanalyst Jacques Lacan, in particular regarding the distinction he makes between the object of desire and the cause of desire, as well as the distinction between need, demand and desire. This analysis will make clear why the autonomy discourse is insufficient to understand how a critical relation to technology is possible. The application power of this view is briefly illustrated by the example of Tinder.

Session Organizer:

Robert Rosenberger, Georgia Institute of Technology

256. Dissolving Boundaries: Creative Practice Meets STS – III

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

This set of experimental sessions brings together poets, artists, and

musicians alongside STS scholarship and STS approaches in order to explore the role of the nonlinear, the nonverbal, the intuitive, and the gestural in deepening our understanding of climate change, the covid pandemic, and mass extinction -- as well as the scientific response to each of these. The sessions also explore art-science collaborations as a way to generate insight into scientific practice and knowledge, and as a pedagogical method. In addition, some sessions explore not-necessarily-academic knowledge and insight developed via creative interaction with other-than-human beings, as well as through intra- and cross-disciplinary blendings of science, STS, and the arts. Presentations will include readings and performances as well as more traditional inquiry. Session 3 of the panel focuses on inter- and cross-disciplinary approaches to creating and interpreting scientific and technical knowledge.

Participants:

Art-Science collaboration and building new sociotechnical imaginaries in orphaned spaces *Mrill Ingram, Center for Integrated Agricultural Studies, UW Madison*

This presentation is informed by a project investigating the routine production of “orphaned space,” and the role of art-science collaboration in expanding relationships with it, including in response to climate change. I define orphaned space as the omnipresent, but mostly overlooked, spaces of infrastructure, as well as spaces of abandonment and contamination. Such spaces are cut off from ecological and social connectivity via active management, such as fencing, cementing, pesticide use, as well as by levels of pollution that inhibit the emergence of diverse relationships. All orphaned spaces perform a role in our ongoing maintenance; many of them also contain histories of struggle and injustice. Such spaces are necessary elements of our infrastructure, but their unsettling lack of discursive visibility calls for new socio-technical practices and a new Earth ethic.

Between-space/s: Towards a Transmedial Practice of Digital Intimacy *Camille Intson, University of Toronto*

This paper discusses and retrospectively analyzes an emergent transmedial performance practice of digital intimacy, which involves facilitating intimate experiences for participants across digital interfaces, and which emerged in the creation of the experimental online creative work between-space (www.between-space2020.co.uk) at the Royal Central School of Speech and Drama's annual Brink [June 2020] Festival. This practice aims to create web-based spaces of dynamic interactivity between bodies, texts, and technologies that generate digitally intimate encounters. With roots in the entangled disciplines of performance, electronic literature, new media, and installation, between-space is billed as an interactive map of a North London flat during the pandemic's first wave. Through an evaluation of the practice's inception and development during the COVID-19 pandemic, I will reflect on how we may conceive of a performative ‘digital intimacy’. By courting a genealogy of theory and practice surrounding the concept, and by revisiting qualitative participant reflections on the practice, I suggest that a digital intimacy is not solely human-to-human but also human-to-object, involving all objects and technologies between the persons involved in dyadic communicative exchange. By further exploring the practice's blurring of boundaries between digital and physical media and the inherent intimacy of the human/computer interaction, I will reflect on future potentialities for digitally intimate performance by interrogating the practice's successes, challenges, and failures.

Reading between the lines: Using literary and musical methods to interpret climate adaptation literature *Christine Wenc, Arts + Literature Laboratory / Greenwood History*

In this presentation, I will show how it is possible to analyze and interpret selections of text from the climate change adaptation scientific and policy literature using literary and musical methods and approaches. My goal is to bring out subjective emotion under this “objective” text, that of both the author and the reader --

emotion and subjectivity which I propose is important when analyzing official responses to climate change and which can provide additional insight when combined with STS approaches. The presentation may include my own subjectivity via a short performance of a song created using these methods.

Session Organizer:

Christine Wenc, Arts + Literature Laboratory / Greenwood History

Chair:

Christine Wenc, Arts + Literature Laboratory / Greenwood History

257. Menstruation as Technology, Technologies of Menstruation

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Participants:

Coping with the moon's revenge: ethnologists and menstruation in fieldwork. *Clarissa Reche*, State University of Campinas - UNICAMP

Menstruation occupies a central role in amerindians cosmopolitics. Menstrual blood is a powerful fluid with psychotropic properties, capable of interfering on processes such as growing food, sorcery, shamanic sessions. Therefore, the menstruated person demands intensive collective care, while this period is a dangerous moment of openness to transformational multiplicity. For most of amazonian amerindians, the threat is human character itself, once menstruation is cosmologically linked to a murder that created both moon and prohibition of incest - basis for all kinship and sociability. Seclusion and diet, if strictly followed, guarantee a safer process of "change of skin" unleashed by bloodletting. Given the Western taboos and connection with Judeo-Christian notion of "wickedness" on menstruation, the anthropological analysis among radical alterities carries a colonial bias of theoretical assumptions about subjugation of women in all cultures. Even feminist perspectives corroborated with this approach, when not just avoided the topic. Following decolonial feminist studies, my proposal is sketch an answer to this question: how ethnologists express their experiences of menstruation during the fieldwork among radical alterities? By searching for these expressions - in academic production, interviews and other experiments - we can highlight: how menstruation figures as an embodied knowledge that has been undermined in scientific work; clashes between situated feminist perspective and intents to build non-colonial relationships in the production of scientific knowledge; the possibility of understanding menstruation as skill and technology, bypassing the violent attempt to allocate it exclusively on nature or culture and tensioning the production of bodies differences

Femtech and the Impact of Emerging Technologies of Menstruation *Laura Shipp*, Royal Holloway, University of London

Millions of menstruators are now using apps and other forms of digital technology to manage and understand their periods - technology that is considered to be part of the 'Femtech' movement. Femtech companies can be described as those making products and services to improve women's health and wellness. Their products, blogs and social media outputs often use feminist language and principles to sell their products and appeal to millennial audiences who may favour such brands over those that take a more closeted approach to menstruation. In doing so, they are perpetuating the construction of menstruation as a problem that produces a market for solutions (Kissling, 2006): pushing tech as the provider of such solutions. The responsibility of a menstruator to manage their individual leakiness continues to be upheld, but this time through the feminist ideals of bodily knowledge, empowerment, and self-care. Through this, these

products and practices contribute to a wider process of individualising, personalising and commercialising healthcare provision in place of delivering inclusive care to all menstruators. The paper is significant to the field of STS as it considers the complex relationships between products, their narratives and the impact these objects are having in the world. It will be drawing on interdisciplinary research, including empirical findings from a virtual ethnography of the Femtech industry, and a series of interviews with Femtech stakeholders and those using their products.

Modern and Empowered but Still Stigmatized: Analyzing the Discourse Surrounding Menstrual Cups *Malissa Kay Shaw*, Taipei Medical University

Menstrual management products (e.g., pads and tampons) have long shaped the ways women manage their menstruation and their menstruating bodies as well as how menstruation is socially constructed. Such products have historically targeted consumers with a discourse of modernity, connecting their use with being modern. An analysis of company websites that produce menstrual cups (MCs), a reusable menstrual technology, identifies a new use of this modern discourse: the interrelationship between "modern women" and female empowerment. Three interconnected discourses of modernity are employed to promote female empowerment. MCs are "modern technologies" themselves, as are their manufacturing processes, the materials used, and the health and environmental awareness they embody. MCs invoke a "modern ideology" in calling on women to actively break the silence surrounding menstruation and explore their bodies and menstrual experiences to eliminate menstrual and bodily shame. Last, MCs promote a "modern lifestyle" (mobile, active, independent) free from menstruation related constraints and able to make informed menstrual management decisions. Here this modern discourse functions as a double-edged sword that paradoxically reinforces negative images of menstruation. When highlighting the advantages of MCs, sometimes existing menstrual stigmas are obliquely endorsed particularly through messages of concealing menstruation and avoiding embarrassment. Furthermore, emphasizing enhanced mobility depicts menstruation as burdensome and even debilitating. The underlying (and occasionally direct) stigmatizing messages within these discourses of modernity and empowerment suggest an enduring interdependence between menstrual products and menstrual shame.

Post-Menstrual Technologies: A Feminist STS History of Stimulating Reproduction *Risa Cromer*, Purdue University

Scientific researchers over the past century actively identified, purified, and developed hormone-based therapies that have been foundational to assisting reproduction. This paper traces a feminist STS history of post-menopausal technologies: the landmark gonadotropic therapeutics, Pergonal and Gonal-F, by the Italian pharmaceutical company Serono. Pergonal is a drug containing follicle stimulating hormone (FSH) and luteinizing hormone (LH) that was derived from menopausal women's urine and designed to assist the reproduction of married white women. In the late 1940s, FSH and LH were extracted and purified by an Italian chemist who inspired an Israeli medical student to convince Pope Pious XII to support a clinical trial, which required urine from hundreds of non-menstruating Catholic nuns. When scaling up production to meet the increasing demand for the popular drug proved challenging, Serono scientists sought alternative sources for the hormones. Using recombinant technology, they developed Gonal-F—a recombinant FSH made by inserting human genes derived from fetal liver cells in the genome of a Chinese hamster ovary cell line, by the billions. By linking the reproductive capacities of diverse bodies across region, religion, time, and species, post-menopausal technologies reveal a phenomenon I describe as stimulating reproduction: the consequential arousal of scientific, clinical, religious, national,

ethical, political, and market investments in assisting reproduction.

Quantifying Experiences of Endometriosis: Menstrual Self-tracking, Chronic Illness and Gendered Subjects in a Nordic Healthcare Context *Venla Oikkonen, Tampere University; Maria Temmes, Tampere University*

Endometriosis is a chronic illness in which cells similar to those in the uterine lining grow outside the uterus in, for example, ovaries, kidneys, intestines, and even lungs, causing chronic pain. Endometriosis tissue responds to changes in hormone levels during the menstrual cycle, and therefore diagnosis and treatment involve tracking pain and other symptoms in relation to menstruation. This paper investigates the introduction of a digital self-tracking app called *Moona Oirepäiväkirja* (*Moona* "symptoms diary") in Finland in 2018. *Moona* was developed through the Finnish gynecological patient organization *Korento*, and it will be included in the "digital treatment path" at a Finnish university hospital; there are also plans to introduce *Moona* in other countries, such as Sweden and Iceland. We focus on materials on *Moona*'s development and framing by the patient organization and clinicians, online accounts by people using the app, as well as the app itself as a digital technology. We ask how an app designed for public healthcare use in the Nordic context is situated in relation to the neoliberal self-tracking market, and how the uses of menstrual self-tracking for a gendered chronic condition differ from the uses of menstrual self-tracking for reproduction and contraception explored by feminist STS scholars. The paper identifies tensions between how the project of quantifying period-associated symptoms helps patients establish the "realness" of illness and their treatment needs in the doctor's office, and how the imperative of self-monitoring may place responsibility with the patient and their circumstances rather than societal and healthcare structures.

Ungendering Menstruation: Nonbinary and Queer STS Approaches to Menstrual Misery and Liberation *Ela Przybylo, Illinois State University*

Since a young age my period has been trying to kill me. In 2002 it got me with Toxic Shock Syndrome and in more chronic ways throughout my menstruating life it has been accompanied by incapacitating pains linked to endometriosis. In this paper, I draw on queer autoethnography (i.e., Preciado; Stewart), crip theory (Kafer; Jones; Przybylo and Fahs), queer and feminist somatechnical approaches to STS (i.e., Bolton; Gill-Peterson; Snorton), and critical menstruation studies (i.e., Bobel; Bobel, Winker, Fahs, Hasson, Kissling, and Roberts), to theorize the queer somatechnics of menstrual suppression. I begin by briefly exploring medical histories, which have often mobilized misogynist fears and hatred of menstruation toward alternately supporting and decrying menstrual suppression. Following on this, I examine the cultural significance for nonbinary identity of the "Tony the Tampon" activist campaign by Cass Clemmer, arguing that it transforms the gender of menstrual bleeding and destigmatizes menstrual blood. Finally, I use my own life experiences to argue that while menstrual positivity can be integral to nonbinary identity, leaving space for acknowledging the trauma and dysphoria of menstruation is equally important. Because menstruation is structurally constructed as something one has to "overcome" and because it is feminized as a "woman's problem," queer and crip somatechnical STS approaches to menstrual management and suppression are integral. I argue for menstrual suppression as an integral component of robust gender affirmation as well as pain and trauma management. Pushing against a medical and consumer model of menstrual bleeding, I call for a theory of menstrual suppression that is gender inclusive, attuned to pain and trauma, and invested in political models of menstruation.

Session Organizer:

Amanda Menking

258. Reflective Engagements With Machine Learning In Healthcare - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

Participants:

Between Senses and Senors: Practicing care in the reassembled ICU *Carsten Horn, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies; Timo Bühler, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies; Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies*

The current situation, a pandemic of global scale, has brought the work of Intensive Care Units (ICUs) to its limits and, subsequently, to the center of attention. The need for a rapid response to increasing cases of severe COVID-19, have led to a re-assembling of the ICU around technological innovations. One such initiative is the research consortium "ICU4Covid" funded by the European Commission that aims at the implementation of telemedical systems connecting the ICUs of "peripheral" and "central" hospitals in order to assure a better distribution of expertise and a remote monitoring of patients' conditions. The implementation of increasingly dense networks of sensors which capture vital data of patients, combined with decision support systems based on artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML) are central elements of this transformation. Going beyond recent discussions on the uses of AI and ML in the healthcare sector, which mainly focus on ethical and legal aspects, we aim to explore how health care practitioners experience and assess these transformations of their work environments in practice. In particular we want to understand the relation of "sensing and sensing" in health care related work, i.e. how the classical medical sensory work (Harris 2021) gets articulated with an increasing presence of sensor delivered data and AI interpretations. We thus ask how they adapt their everyday practices of knowing and decision-making, how they navigate the field of tensions between seeming data-based certainties and uncertainties of clinical decision-making and how they rethink the distribution of responsibility.

Mapping Gordian Knots In Developing Fair ML Tools For Healthcare *Renate Baumgartner, Eberhard Karls Universität Tübingen*

Artificial intelligence (AI) and machine learning (ML) are seen as big hope within the field of medicine. Algorithmic tools including ML are framed as being a key feature for overcoming future challenges of healthcare, such as helping to reduce costs that may result from an aging population and fewer health care professionals being available. Some also anticipate ML could lead to more equality in health care, as it seems more objective than humans. Hopes are high, however, before ML will be able to show which influence it has, different aspects should be considered. Scientists and stakeholders pledging for ethical ML usually take into account fairness, accountability, transparency and robustness as key features. Many statisticians claim, that statistically we have all we need to make ML fair. I claim, however, that there are still different Gordian knots that should be considered (or tried to solve) when tackling the endeavour of developing ML in a way that ensures social equality. In this talk I would like to map out two of those knots that could also be described as "aporia", problems that cannot be solved, because it lies in their very nature to be unsolvable. One knot is what I call "the privacy vs. participation dilemma". It means only people whose data is part of the training data for ML will in the end have been considered for the end product. This stands in crass contrast to privacy issues, which are especially salient for people who are part of a minority population. Thus, the dilemma is: either one will provide their data or one will not be considered within the tool. This raises ethical questions above all for groups

who (for good reasons) might not want to share their data or are statistically too small to be taken into account, such as intersex and transgender people. The second knot is the re-introduced tension between social constructivist and poststructuralist approaches vs. materialist approaches. ML usually works with strict categories. Therefore, bringing ML into certain fields means old categories are being reproduced, but also new categories might emerge. Considering constructivist and poststructuralist understandings of categories, which focus on the social construction and deconstruction of categories, the introduction of ML and its mechanisms of categorization, classification and objectification should be watched with critical eyes. Within medicine, this prompts known questions of naturalization of categories, such as gender and race, which feminist science and technology studies worked on relentlessly to deconstruct. On the other side: how can specific groups of people be considered within an ML-tool without using categories? What is the role of materialist approaches and strategic essentialism? Are there possibilities to develop more fluid categories? I suggest these questions should be openly discussed. Different stakeholders (including patients) should be involved in the decision processes of which ML we would like to have and for what purposes it should be used.

Relating To Epistemic Responsibility: The Machine Learning Entanglements Of Ten Mental Healthcare Organizations
Marthe Stevens, iHub, Radboud University Nijmegen; Anne Beaulieu, University of Groningen

Machine learning (ML) models are being developed to play a role in the treatment of patients and organization of care. The models are created in complex environments made up of humans, technologies and organizations. Here, technologies, knowledge, knowers are all interdependent, rather than one being the result of the other. In such a setting, the notion of responsibility needs rethinking, since individualized conceptions of responsibility are increasingly difficult to uphold. In this presentation, we put forth a notion of epistemic responsibility in relation to ML, based on Bellacasa's work on care (2017). We ethnographically followed Dutch healthcare professionals that learned the basics of (supervised) ML while pursuing a project in their organizations during a four-month ML course. The learning that took place made both the struggles and pleasures of the professionals with the different interdependencies visible and brought responsibility-in-the-making into relief. Rather than seeing (growing) connections and impure entanglements as standing in the way of responsibility, we see these connections as worthy of inquiry. We argue that connections are essential to knowing and, that producing responsibility means considering these embedded relations. This enables us to take a novel approach to what it means to develop algorithms responsibly.

Wading Through A 'Swamp Of Rules': Regulatory Ambiguity And Machine Learning Experiments In Healthcare
Rik Wehrens, Erasmus University; Marthe Stevens, iHub, Radboud University Nijmegen; Johanna Kostenzer, Erasmus University; Anne Marie Weggelaar, Erasmus University; Antoinette De Bont, Erasmus University

In recent years, machine learning applications have taken central stage as promissory technologies that are accompanied with dreams about personalized and preventive medicine. Following these developments, STS scholars have raised major ethical questions (e.g. concerning epistemology, bias, surveillance, and opacity of data infrastructures). While recognizing the importance of ethical reflection, this presentation builds from another starting point. We followed 12 hospital-based pilots in data-driven technologies in 8 European countries at a moment when the EU General Data Protection Regulation became effective. We focused on the regulatory ambiguity within such projects and the consequences for machine learning experiments in healthcare. Based on 145 semi-structured interviews and 5

focus groups, we develop the metaphor of a 'swamp of rules' as a way to reflect on the misalignments between rules and practices as they were experienced across the pilots by technicians, data scientists, clinicians and policymakers. We distinguish four recurrent instantiations of this perceived 'swamp of rules': regulatory layering, regulatory complexity, regulatory ambivalence and regulatory uncertainty. We also distinguish various consequences: risk-avoidant behavior, proceduralism, and the introduction of new experts. We found that rules become more complicated whenever data becomes 'fluid': when it has to travel beyond the institution, move across international boundaries, becomes placed in a new category, or used in new contexts. Notably, all consequences hampered further uptake of data-driven technologies and reduced clinical relevance. We reflect on these results in the light of ongoing discussions about ethical principles, regulatory pressure, discretionary spaces and resilience.

Session Organizer:

Heta Tarkkala, University of Eastern Finland

259. 6S Open Meeting

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

The 6S Open Meeting (also known as the Business Meeting) welcomes anyone who is interested in 6S (the student section of 4S)--no prior involvement or experience necessary! Come to hear about 6S activities, ways to get involved, or simply connect with other STS students.

Session Organizers:

Katie Ulrich, Rice University

Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine

Misria Shaik Ali, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Chairs:

Misria Shaik Ali, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine

Katie Ulrich, Rice University

260. Sea and Soil: Connecting Agriculture and Aquaculture

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This panel puts in conversation research on food politics as it connects across soil science and aquaculture. Soil scientists wrestling with climate change, fertilizer practices and its relation to soil sustainability, Cannabis growing that shifts understanding of agriculture, and aquaculture practices that shape fish and waters alike: this panel looks at relationships between science and policy practices as they express themselves through soil and sea.

Participants:

Changing epistemic commitments of a research field? Soil sciences and its orientation towards global challenges
Lisa Sigl, Research Platform Responsible Research and Innovation in Academic Practice, University of Vienna; Ruth Falkenberg, University of Vienna; Maximilian Fochler, University Of Vienna

Soil and its relevance for global issues like climate change or food security have gained increasing public and policy attention within the past two decades (e.g. seven soil functions of the EU 2006, Year of Soil 2015). This development is accompanied by reflections within parts of the soil sciences about whether soil scientists are ready to "rise to the occasion and play a clear role in major research programs on issues dealing with sustainable development" (Bouma 2009). To live up to this challenge, we currently see ongoing deliberations within the soil science community about how to become more responsive to societal challenges and contribute to solving global problems in actual practices of soil science research. This development has in the meantime amongst others spawned attempts to set research priorities by international soil science organisations, the

foundation of new scientific journals, discussions around which scientific concepts can serve this purpose best and the development of new research practices. Building on exploratory document analysis, analyses of discussion papers and commentaries in relevant journals, and interviews with soil scientists who have taken a prominent role in these developments, we discuss in how far this move towards relevance can be described as an intellectual / scientific movement (Frickel/Gross 2005) and what aspects were particularly important for supporting and shaping it. Further, we aim to explore in how far these developments are seen as generating a new self-understanding of soil scientists, in the sense that it changes their epistemic commitments (Granjou/Arpin 2015).

Fishing in toxic waters?: Transitioning technoscience, practices and the environment in Greek aquacultures *Stathis Arapostathis, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens; Konstantinos Vattes, Kapodistrian University of Athens*

The paper studies the co-production (Jasanoff, 2010) of Greek aquacultures of sea bass and sea bream with environmental policies and politics since the 1980s. Greece is globally first in the production of sea bass and one of the strongest producers in sea bream. In both the Aegean and the Ionian Sea aquacultures have acquired the character of intensive monocultures that suffer of major pathogens. Incumbent regime actors responded to challenges that are related to fish's well-being by establishing integrated systems of farming that have been accompanied by AM-based treatment regimens. The challenges posed by the pathogens co-produced with challenges that were emerged due to visions and aspirations for market profits and the creation of a whole industrial sector. Sociotechnical imaginaries promote technical fixes that would enhance fish quality and enable environmental sustainability (Jasanoff and Kim, 2013). New breeds are introduced, and their effectiveness and valorization have been co-produced with new plant-based feeds, medication and vaccines. The entanglements of feed-stock enhancement, breed selection and chemicalization of production define the ontological politics of fishes, configure regime transitions while at the same time shape the context of transition politics and contestation. The questions we address are: What have been the processes of coproduction of the industrialized aquaculture with the large-scale infrastructures and programs of fish breeding? In what way have political priorities and sociotechnical imaginaries configured the valorization of techno- scientific solutions in the Greek aquacultures? The paper is based on primary archival research and series of interviews with stakeholders.

Flourishing in Unregulated Spaces: How Cannabis Accepts Uncertainty in Ways Traditional Agriculture May Not *Marie F Turner, Colorado State University; Erika Amethyst Szymanski, Colorado State University*

In Cannabis, unregulated agriculture has created places of ignorance (Durant, 2020), but also fostered niche flourishes of agricultural microbiome products and knowledges. Though denied production of the formal knowledge networks that support other row and specialty crops, Cannabis cultivators have also had to develop unconventional knowledges to solve their problems. For example, only recently, have any pesticides been listed for legal use in Cannabis. This delay has, on the one hand, resulted in widespread illegal use of dangerous chemicals, but, has also driven a creative niche market of multispecies microbe-based products in the following way: Because these products have been developed in a sort of symbiogenesis with the once completely illicit Cannabis market, researchers and developers in this space have been less concerned with the mechanism- and identity-based regulatory framework applied to products in traditional cultivation systems (which has largely driven the development of chemicals and single-strain biologicals). We interviewed product

developers and growers who confirmed that frameworks of regulation and difficulties in quality controlling the emergent properties of multispecies microbiome products help to reinforce their absence in legal, regulated spaces of agriculture, whereas in Cannabis, uncertainty about mechanism and content has been less important than something that simply works. This suggests unregulated spaces may work to co-produce valuable knowledges (Jasanoff, 2004) that go otherwise ignored or unexamined under traditional agriculture's need for mechanistic understandings and predictability.

Session Organizer:

Lisa Sigl, Research Platform Responsible Research and Innovation in Academic Practice, University of Vienna

261. COVID-19 National and Transnational Narratives and Imaginaries

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Though a global pandemic, state and scientific responses to COVID-19 have developed via particular nation-state and national policy and techno-scientific conditions, even as the scope or research and responses, from vaccines to animal trafficking is transnational in scope. This panel takes up this simultaneously national and transnational scope of COVID-19 techno-scientific responses to consider the transnational use of Big Data from multinationals, the generation of science denialism via Facebook, comparative vaccine rollouts, the East to West flows of Pangolin research, as well as the ways of imaginatively figuring COVID-19 between the ontologies of Chinese medicine and Australian manifestation of pandemic.

Participants:

Mass behavior and the effect of governmental health measures from a perspective of big data in the age of COVID-19
Guoyan Wang, Soochow University

Governmental health measures have profound impacts on public behavior since the beginning of the COVID-19 epidemic. Through computational method, this paper analyzed both the big data on mass behavior and governmental health measures from three typical countries with severe epidemic situation in the initial stage: China, Italy, and the United States. Big data were taken from databases provided by multiple authorities, including Baidu, Alibaba, Google and Apple. Three types of big data reflecting behavioral changes were selected as index of, epidemic concern, self-protection, and mobility trends. Totally 490 items of health measures released by governmental and authoritative health agency websites were collected as well. We revealed a three-phase rule of public behavior in outbreak of epidemic, namely the wait-and-see phase, the surge phase and the slow release phase. Further, this research uncovers and analyzes the Surge phenomenon. Either when the epidemic is described as serious or mobility restrictions are stringent, the outflow of population from the epidemic area will be accelerated in a short time, forming a Surge. Also it was found that strict mobility restrictions are more likely to cause a surge of population outflow from the epidemic area in the short term, whereas the effect of mobility restrictions is positively related to their stringency in the long term. The social and cultural differences among the various countries are important factors that influence the effects of the governments' health measures.

Translating, Narrating And Communicating 'Wen bing' Pandemic Outbreak In Melbourne, Australia is Ushering in a Transmodern Spacetime World Order
Rey Tiquia, University of Melbourne

Together with the concepts of the Yin and Yang, Five Elements, I see qi as an ontological entity or imaginary. It can be seen as an 'imaging figure, a metaphor or a narrative that has realness achieved in the emergence of gradually clotting and eventually routinized, sets of embodied, in-place actions.' [Helen Verran. (2005)]. Imaginaries, imaging figures and narratives can be seen as similar to Foucault's epistemes, Kuhn's paradigms, Callon,

Law and Latour's actor-networks, Hacking's self-vindicating constellations, Fujimura and Star's standardized packages and boundary objects and Knorr-Cetina's reconfiguration," David Turnbull's 'assemblage, and Donna Haraway's 'vision metaphor.' And an assemblage is a translation medium. Viewed from this perspective, an 'incubating qi' can be seen as an expression of the natural yin and yang order of the flow and metamorphoses of 'life' embedded in specific time and place i.e. the life of the influenza virus or coronavirus embedded within the human body. The 'outbreak narrative' of wenbing (influenza) 'as seen by contemporary practitioners of Chinese medicine is a collective term for disorders that Western biomedicine classifies as acute febrile diseases. These are primarily characterized by high fever and by their infectious nature, as with typhoid and typhus. In premodern China however, wenbing were seen as encompassing a range of illnesses from the common colds, to high fevers and epidemic diseases, all of which were characterized by acute fevers and hot sensations in the patient's body. Chinese medical doctrine attributes these disorders to pathogenic heat of varying quality from warm (wen 温) to hot (re 熱), which is characteristic of the climate in spring and summer respectively (Hanson, 1998). And as COVID-19 spreads globally, and as we act in accordance with the 'seasonal, geographical and personal factors,' how should we in Australia and the rest of the world deal with it (coronavirus) in our local real time situation? According to the late Joseph Needham we should use acupuncture or chronoacupuncture's 'immunological' and 'cortisone-like effect' to fight the invading organism by strengthening the patient's body resistance.

What Pangolins Tell Us About People: Pandemic Representations in US Print Media *Juliet Tempest, Stanford University*

The pangolin has captured media attention in the US for mediating between the bodies of others during Covid-19, ever since a Chinese university research team announced the pangolin as potential intermediary host of the SARS-CoV-2 virus' transmission to humans. As the world's most heavily trafficked mammal, the pangolin has thus become a discursive and material site of investigation into the pandemic's origins in China. Using a critical discourse-informed thematic analysis, I trace historical and contemporary depictions of pangolins in US print news media, to reveal trends of scapegoating the charismatic non-Western and non-human Other that affect our ability to apprehend pandemics: the narrative of "blame" in criticizing the Other distracts us from our common task of critiquing the problem to find a solution. In the tradition of science and technology studies, this paper highlights another directionality for the translation of science—from East to West—where studies of flows in the opposite direction have predominated. Media representations of pangolins suggest different treatments of systems of "Chinese science": biomedical epidemiology as international, even Occidentalized, and only "Traditional" Chinese Medicine as "Chinese." Engaging with intersecting levels and theories of mediation—of viruses between bodies, of knowledge by the news, and of pangolins across both—I propose to show that the pangolin's material and discursive indeterminacy mediated the US media's translation of Chinese science about its role as zoonotic intermediary.

From Vaccine Diplomacy to Vaccine Equity: Comparing the Strategies of Israel and India *Pnina Geraldine Abir-Am, Brandeis University*

In the unequal and uncertain worlds currently surrounding the unprecedented, year long, Covid-19 pandemic, very few countries have an adequate vaccine supply. Most countries continue to vaccinate their populations at unsatisfactory rates, a situation which prolongs the pandemic and its terrible costs in human lives, social suffering, and economic loss. Having become world leaders in the manufacturing of generic drugs, Israel and

India are not only leading the vaccine rollout but are capable of helping other countries, usually by donating vaccines. Israel was able to obtain priority for the Pfizer vaccine by granting it access to data necessary to validate its vaccine. This data was available in Israel due to its comprehensive, digitalized medical records and pervasive health infrastructure. India, on the other hand, manufactured the AstraZeneca vaccine under specific license for distribution to lower income countries, in up to date facilities such as the Serum Institute of India. The talk compares the strategies used by Israel and India in accessing the vaccine and analyzes the policies used to determine which countries to help. The talk also examines issues of vaccine equity as both countries engaged in vaccine diplomacy, rewarding countries they seek to influence) but refrained from helping neighbors with whom they have political territorial disputes. Those neighbors also refrained from asking India and Israel for help because they preferred to obtain the vaccine from other sources such as WHO, Russia, or China. This case study suggests how STS oriented policy analysis can help extract guidelines so that an equitable and fast distribution of the vaccine takes precedence over political disputes.

Session Organizer:
Guoyan Wang, Soochow University

262. The Work of Gender

5:00 to 6:30 pm
4S 2021 Virtual: 22

This panel brings together research that investigates the work of gender in technoscience. It includes paper that take on questions of labor directly, such as the gendered labor of quality control protocols, or female entrepreneurship, or the marketing of menstrual cups, as well as research that investigates how "gender" as a concept is produced renegotiated, such as in patient-expert relations in gender affirming health care.

Participants:

Gender and high-technology entrepreneurship in São Paulo, Brazil *Camila Dias Rigolin, Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCAR, Brazil)*

This study investigated female-technology-based entrepreneurship or the relationship between gender and innovation in small companies characterized by the intensive application of technical-scientific knowledge in the design, development and production of new products and processes. Investigating the profile of the entrepreneurs allows a more accurate diagnosis of possible distortions and conflicts associated with the gender issue in the creation and establishment of businesses, as well as the identification of patterns, strategies and coping devices that can subsidize projects, programs and public policies aimed at promoting gender equity in technology-based entrepreneurship. We analyzed 189 technology-based companies run by women in the state of São Paulo, Brazil, supported by a governmental funding agency. The numbers of female participation in technology-based entrepreneurship in Brazil confirm international data related to female underrepresentation associated with the STEM areas. The scientific production of the directors, accounted for by the number of papers published in journals is quite expressive, reflecting the large number of coordinators who hold a PhD degree. Technological production, counting the numbers of patents and utility models, is more than ten times lower. Pharmaceutical Sciences lead the areas of training for women entrepreneurs, followed by Chemistry and Biology. The lack of women in engineering and computing is expressive. In the medium term, the under-representation of women in these areas represents a blackout of qualified human resources, reduces the quantity and diversity of the workforce engaged in research and development and compromises the innovation potential of organizations, knowledge areas, economic sectors, regions and even countries.

How matters of concern invade technologies: The case of the

menstrual cup *Franck Cochoy, Université Toulouse Jean-Jaurès - LISST-CERS*

Feminine care products represent a well-suited case to illustrate the evolution from classic to concerned markets—i.e. markets that focus not only on economic efficiency and the utilitarian matching between supply and demand but also on the negative externalities produced by market products and exchanges (Geiger et al. 2014). The menstrual cup is a good example to address such matters. This device has supplemented tampons and sanitary pads, and if the original focus on practical and material dimensions remains (absorbency, lightness, smallness, disposability, etc.), new concerns have invaded the scene. Significantly, in the advertisements for menstrual cups, reusability, recyclability, safety, or hypoallergenic issues have replaced the past quest for efficiency and feeling carefree. Thus, the following questions are raised: What has fueled the evolution from pads and tampons to cups? How have matters of facts and matters of concern been involved? I propose to address these questions with a multi-method approach. In Section 1, based on firsthand and secondhand historical data, I show that for a long time, environmental and health issues played no or little role in the promotion of cups. In the following sections, I rely on digital methods to analyze the corpus consisting of 5,235 consumer reviews (posted on Amazon.com) about the Star Cup (pseudonym), a leading product on the market for menstrual cups.

Sorting Women: The Gendered Work of Quality Control
Aleksandra Kaminska, U de Montréal; Alysse Verona Kushinski

This paper explores the labour of enacting quality control protocols as a crucial moment on the production line, arguing that the process of sorting the well-made from the substandard can be considered through the historical and conceptual lens of “women’s work” (Cohn 2018). We focus on the security printing industry and its manufacturing of official papers, such as stamps and banknotes, and draw on materials from the Bank of England archives, Library Archives Canada, and the US Bureau of Engraving and Printing, to show women as the ultimate checkers, verifiers and examiners of such papers. We argue that the tasks of quality control precede and inform the office-based clerical duties that are today more commonly associated with “women’s work,” and reflect the repetitious and monotonous nature of feminized labour (Elson and Pearson 1981). We also account for the long standing role of women in the paper industry, including their work as rag pickers and sorters in the mills of the 19th century (Craig 2019). While integral to scientific management and efficient production, quality control has been understudied in fields such as STS, even while feminist STS has paved the way for exploring techno-social arrangements of women’s occupational roles and contributions to technology (Liparito 1994, Light 1999, Evans 2018). The activities of sorting and quality control show how women’s labour in information and technology production has been varied, historical, and continuous, and ultimately provide another case for considering the ongoing replacement of traditionally feminized roles and tasks with machine automation (Keilty 2017).

Toxic Measurements: Justifying Gendered Intervention *Paula Martin*

Contemporary gender affirmative medicine is haunted by toxic histories of individual and institutional pathologization. Manifest in clinical procedures of diagnosis and assessment, the epistemic relation between expert and patient has often undercut the possibility of self-definition, especially in the case of youth. In turn, this has limited the ability of individuals to access interventions like hormones and surgery. In the United States, providers at my primary fieldside suggest that the only way to know someone’s gender is to ask. Yet this simple question continually fails to supply the necessary evidence to justify

intervention in the face of those attempting to halt the provision of care to minors. This paper examines relationships between historical ways of knowing and treating gender and current efforts to surpass those patterns. Such efforts attempt to cultivate new relational models between medical experts and their patients, which entails reckoning with what can, and cannot, be known about individual experiences of gender. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork at scientific conferences and with a clinical research team studying early intervention into gender, I demonstrate that in order to gesture towards a future which is fundamentally unknowable, and to assuage doubts about the legitimacy of intervention, researchers and clinicians often reproduce problematic logics of gender through the tools they use to measure and assess. Such tools bring along harmful histories, carrying the toxicity of the past into the present, and projecting it into the future.

Session Organizer:

Franck Cochoy, Université Toulouse Jean-Jaurès - LISST-CERS

263. Medical Care Politics

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

This panel stages a conversation between research that investigates the protocols and circulation of medical care research. From thyroid studies of children in Fukushima Prefecture, to UK public health practices around monitoring sexually transmitted infections, to the practice of nasogastric tube feeding in Taiwan . AS well as papers that directly investigate medical care protocols policies, such as conflict of interest policies in Belgian medical schools or the shifting representation of drug use in Norway. The panel gathers work that demonstrates how policies, protocols, and practices shift the terms of health care.

Participants:

Conflict of Interest Policies at Belgian Medical Faculties:

Cross-Sectional Study Indicates Little Oversight *Lucas Bechoux, Université de Liège (SPIRAL); François Thoreau, Spiral, University of Liege*

As a place where medical knowledge is formed, medical schools face multiple influences. They play a crucial role in preparing student to future interactions with the pharmaceutical industry. As little information is available on the situation in Belgium, we undertook an assessment of conflict of interest policies at Belgian medical schools. We searched the website of the ten Belgian medical schools in November 2019 with standardized keywords. The deans of medicine were invited to participate by providing us with further information. We also consulted personal contacts within faculties among students and teachers. Based on a list of 15 criteria, we calculated a total for each faculty with a maximum score of 30 points. By December 2019, we had gathered policies for four faculties. In all cases, these policies consisted of “moderate” initiatives with little or no “restrictive” elements. Only one faculty showed interest in our study by providing us with relevant information. The maximum score obtained was 3 out of 30 points with six faculties scoring 0. Our results show that there is still some way to go to ensure a medical training independent from pharmaceutical industry for future Belgian physicians. Similar studies in the United-States and France had a positive impact on the management of COI at medical schools. It made the problem exist within society and pushed the academic authorities to take more restrictive measures. We see this study as a lever for the establishment of clearer management policies of influence in Belgian medical training.

Greying with an “Elephant Trunk”: The Controversies of Nasogastric Feeding in Elderly Care in Taiwan *Anne-chie Wang*

There is an arguably medical issue about using nasogastric tube feeding in elderly care. According to the national survey, there are 197 thousand Taiwanese using nasogastric tube feeding per

year, which is 5 times higher than Japan. The controversies of prolonged nasogastric feeding arise because people's concerns may disturb the elderly's quality of life. This study investigates why does the nasogastric tube feeding distinctly prevails in Taiwan, while other countries prefer to use a gastrostomy tube as ways of artificial feeding. Furthermore, how does it become an option to withdraw or withhold at the end of life care in the legal frame? Probing this issue could reveal how the medical technology involved may help to improve life quality for the seniors. The study adopts the content analysis method to analyze the documents produced by the Ministry of Health and Welfare and the content of the Legislative Yuan Gazette from 2000 to 2018 about the discussion the impact of artificial nutri and on life quality. And the researcher did the participant observation in a palliative hospice ward in a medical center from August 2019 in order to probe the elderly caring process. Besides observing the working in the ward, the researcher also observed the caring process of hospice home care, hospice shared care and outpatient service. The result found that the provision of artificial nutrition and hydration become an option in an advanced directive after the Patient Autonomy Act passed in 2015. It presupposes people as a reasonable citizen following the logic of choice. However, using the feeding tube is not only implicate the nutrition intake but also involve in social value and the normativity of technology.

Mapping infections in inner city populations: care in sexual health in England *Ulla McKnight, University of Sussex; Catherine Marijke Will, University of Sussex*

In this paper we explore the ways in which different local trusts within the national health service respond to the categories used to describe the distribution of a number of sexually transmitted diseases when identifying patients as priorities for certain tests. Drawing on a body of epidemiological and public health research which maps infection risk onto different racialised categories, as well as their intersections with gender, sexuality and sexual history, we note the difficulty for health care professionals in navigating this as primarily a matter of cost containment. Staff cannot order tests unless patients 'fit into' categories but worry that testing practices might be stigmatising or racist. Careful negotiation of these issues which do not have a unified definition, leads some to attempt questions about people's sexual partners or place of birth, while others explicitly choose to avoid the area as too uncomfortable. Making it a matter of 'ethnicity' is a common UK resolution of the race issue, but also allows staff to locate themselves in debates about the proper role of sexual health, which mixes public health and clinical modes of working.

Mass media coverage of the Fukushima thyroid survey *Midori Aoyagi, National Institute for Environmental Studies*

In March 2011, the accident at the TEPCO's Fukushima Daiichi Nuclear Power Station resulted in the spread of radioactivity in the upper atmosphere. After the Chernobyl accident, thyroid cancer occurred frequently in children living in the vicinity of the plant, and it was pointed out that the same cancer could occur in children in Fukushima Prefecture. For this reason, a thyroid survey for children has been conducted since October 2011. Children of the target age who live in Fukushima Prefecture are examined at school if they are of school age, and at the nearest medical institution if they are not. After 10 years, the incidence of thyroid cancer among children in Fukushima Prefecture is not high. At present, some experts are calling for its cancellation. This paper analyzes the differences in newspaper reports on the opinions on thyroid tests between two newspapers: one is a local newspaper in Fukushima prefecture and the other is a national newspaper with subscribers all over Japan. In the analysis, we compare the chronological changes in 1) quantitative analysis (number of related reports in time series, frequency of occurrence of frequent words, etc.) and 2) content analysis (sources of information, tone of the argument, etc.) between the two newspapers to find out the movements behind them. The

significance from the viewpoint of the researcher regarding the continuation of scientific testing, the judgment as a researcher from the viewpoint of the child's life, and the anxiety of the child's parents are intertwined in the situation.

News Media Portrayal Of Drug Use As A Problem In Norway (1965-2004) *Anne Sigrid Lindblad Stokke, University of Oslo*

Following the introduction and establishment of new substances to the drug scenes in Norway in the 1960s, the national health authorities and others raised the question of how to deal with the growing problem of drug use and protect the youth. Around year 2000, another debate about societal reactions to drug use and treatment of drug users had arisen – ultimately leading to the Substance Treatment Reforms in 2004. In Norway and internationally, historical scholarship has analysed the shifts between health approaches and penal approaches to drug use, highlighting competing and sometimes allied processes of medicalisation and criminalisation. A less studied actor in these processes is the news media, which is vital to communicating debates, bringing specific problems to the fore and oftentimes producing the terms of the debate. The primary aim of this project is therefore to study the portrayal of drug use as a problem in Norway in the mentioned periods. The project explores political and societal views on cannabis (and other drugs) and analyses the prohibition debate through the lens of the news media. Framing theory is a means of analysis in media science, and part of this project is to explore the usefulness of framing theory in studying drug use in the media. Another aim of this project is to compare the two periods in question. (How) do these two periods differ with regards to how the problem of drug use as a problem was described by the media?

Session Organizer:

Anne Sigrid Lindblad Stokke, University of Oslo

264. The Prediction Factor: Medical Decision in the Age of Big Data - III: Prediction and Reconfiguration : the use of Big Data in oncology

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

This session will focus on the introduction of Big Data in healthcare, which has had a strong resonance in oncology. Big Data has raised hopes of predicting cancer occurrence and improving treatment. The quest for prediction has led to various reconfigurations in oncology departments and beyond, resulting in changes in data categorisation, daily medical practice and patient care. This data-driven approach to cancer management is not free of illusions related to the use and scope of the techniques developed.

Participants:

Trends in Recent Studies about AI in Breast Cancer Screening and Prediction *Gaurav Pai, University of Washington*

Globally, breast cancer is the most common cancer in women and healthcare researchers have been vigorously experimenting with Artificial Intelligence (AI) towards its early screening, detection, risk identification and prognostic prediction. In the past two years itself, multiple studies that operate in this broad spectrum have been published in journals: A majority of them were based in the US including those by MIT CSAIL, NYU, Google Research, DeepHealth and the DM DREAM Challenge. My paper does a comparative study of these U.S. based studies: While all research found the inclusion of AI to assist radiologists useful, the limited diversity of datasets used in the studies hampers any substantial moves towards a real world acceptance or use of this technology. I argue that lack of a national screening program for breast cancer in the US (in the absence of a national health scheme) makes any one size fits all approach impossible. While the US FDA has recently taken the first steps towards approving a Software as Medical Device (SaMD) regime, a moderately advanced AI tool that could be approved by the regulator is still years away, and that more rigorous evaluation among different racial and ethnic populations could be

the first step towards its widespread acceptance in the US and beyond. My presentation considers the use of AI in breast cancer screening and prediction modalities as a part of Weibe E. Bijker's foundational STS formulation of the social construction of a technology over its life: artifacts → technological system → sociotechnical ensemble → technological culture.

Categorization In Data-driven Research On Breast Cancer

Melanie Goisauf, University of Vienna

Big Data, machine learning (ML) and artificial intelligence (AI) are gaining importance in the medical field as they are expected to improve accuracy and efficiency in diagnosis and treatment. Such data driven approaches and technologies are impacting the way knowledge is produced and decisions are made. Big Data research implies that knowledge production is mainly inductive, neglecting that data is not produced free of preceding theoretical framing, societal categorizations and implications, methodological decisions, technological conditions and the interpretation of correlations. Genomic analysis as well as training and validating of ML algorithms with specific datasets and populations are constituted by practices of defining, interpreting, categorizing, classifying, labelling, and annotating. Based on ongoing qualitative research on breast cancer, this paper reflects on how categorizations are used in data-intensive genomic research and in the development of artificial intelligence (AI) systems in radiology, where genomic sequencing and screening using AI in image-analysis are becoming important predictive tools in diagnostics.

The pathologist in the era of Precision Medicine : a critical success factor of the revolution in oncology? *Audrey Vézian, CNRS - Triangle*

The rise of Precision Medicine is revolutionising oncology. Indeed, the development of next-generation sequencing (NGS) has introduced major changes in medical research and clinical practice. The search for cancer genome alterations made faster and easier by this technique NGS, producing more and more data on tissue. In order to ensure equal access to innovative and existing treatments throughout France, the public authorities have supported the implementation of NGS as part of routine clinical practice both in public and private sectors. Thus, the efforts of public authorities are translated into a reconfiguration and an extensive division of labor between different categories of actors (clinicians, pathologists, molecular biologists, bioinformaticians etc.) and established a national network to allow an equal access to innovation. By adopting a perspective on organizational sociology, sociology of professions and sociology of work, our approach consists in addressing access to NGS tests by focusing on the interactions underlying the decision to accomplish them. By conducting semi-structured interviews, we have described the organizational arrangements for accessing diagnoses based on NGS technology, and the place occupied by different actors in these arrangements. We have characterized concrete exchange and bargaining relations between different stakeholders in order to identify factors which influence the negotiations. We demonstrate that the context of centralisation of molecular analytical skills - detachment from the patient's body, movement and management of the equipment by professionals spread over the territory, support for exchange/interaction within various professional configurations - raise a whole range of ethical questions beyond the simple porosity between care and research. More precisely, we identify the key role of pathologist in order to achieve an optimal territorial articulation of expertise and care, and the material conditions guaranteeing the continuity of exchanges between professionals in the sector.

The Impacts of Big Data and AI Instruments on Radiology *Léo Mignot, Université de Bordeaux - Centre Emile Durkheim*

Far from being a mere promise, applications of AI to oncology imaging are already taking shape and some AI solutions are concretely encapsulated in instruments for tumour detection,

contouring of targets or in recent developments in radiomics. The field of medical imaging in oncology therefore appears to be a very appropriate field of investigation in order to circumscribe the conditions of emergence of AI techniques in the biomedical field and also to identify the social and epistemic effects of their implementation. We propose to analyse AI computer-assisted diagnostic systems (CADs) used in oncology for mammographic screening and cancer prediction in order to see which actors were involved in their development, and what are the logics of interdisciplinary but also intersectoral (science / industry / medicine) collaboration in which these actors are involved. We propose here to examine the thesis that these new techniques have important effects on the social and epistemic organization of imaging oncology and more precisely on three levels: 1/ the question of the preservation of the domain of jurisdiction (Abbott, 1988) of medical specialties and their borders; 2/ the internal organization of services and the division of tasks; 3/ the practice of the actors and their relations with patients. Using the results obtained through the analysis of publications (scientometrics and critical review) and interviews with radiologists and members of the medical industry, it will thus be necessary to determine the effects of AI implementation on the redefinition of expertise, the distribution of tasks between the different specialties mobilized in oncology and on patient care.

Session Organizer:

Margo Bernelin, CNRS - Université de Nantes

265. Becoming with Water: Ethnographic and Methodological Reconifications — II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Water assembles the city around it. It gathers and disrupts publics, infrastructures, temporalities, and capitalistic flows. This panel methodologically peruses the insistence and inevitability of water to merge with, and in so doing, delves into how entangling encounters shape the city itself. City, too, is parsed down as the authors take us through galleries, restaurants, riverside parks, desolate streets, and mountainsides. The papers' invitation to witness micromoments ask us to imagine with the authors a pause to the seemingly headlong pace of the technoscientific urban project and to instead linger on a street or staring into a glass of water. In lingering, this panel contributes to a sensorial and aesthetic turn in STS theory.

Participants:

From Entering The Water To Bringing The River Into The Gallery: Tracing The River Yamuna In Delhi *Aaradhana Dalmia, Delhi School of Economics, Delhi University*

As the city of Delhi has grown, it has built massive infrastructure projects wherein the River Yamuna, flowing through the centre of the city, remains forgotten or kept aside. Despite infrastructural pressure from all sides which hides the river, the Yamuna continues to attract residents of the city and the water enters spaces that one would imagine remain closed to it. Taking examples of the water inviting in and the water being invited in, this paper explores how no matter the effort to physically and visually separate the river and the city, there are existing and emergent ways in which the two continue to intertwine. Firstly, I study the water-based rituals of the festival of "Chhatha", when devotees throng the banks of the River Yamuna to stand in its waters for hours from sunset to sunrise. Secondly, I study how artists across the city have brought the forgotten river into their studios and art galleries and thus once again into the lives and conversations of people. This tracing of the Yamuna in Delhi allows us to move beyond an understanding of rivers or other non-human species as objects that must be controlled and manipulated, towards the idea that bodies such as rivers and their waters are fluid, transforming, and the city and the river are tightly enmeshed and continue to influence one another. Our role is then to trace each strand, see how they unfold and inform a new way of imagining the relationship between non-human and

human actors.

Who's public, who's problem?: Affective encounters with snow in uncertain times *Ariana Seferiades Prece, Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA); Melina Campos Ortiz, Concordia University; Emma Bider, Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA)*

This paper examines the relationship of Montreal's inhabitants with snow and the ways "publics" take shape around it. We examine snow's disruptive potentiality as a material that impedes mobility, affects the expected rhythm of city life, but also generates spontaneous, seasonal and affective publics. Following de Laet and Mol (2000), we suggest that snow is a "fluid" material that shapes relations of control, management, and affection. Using walking as an ethnographic method, we explore the fluid nature of snow both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic paying attention to virtual connections "that span the material and the actual on the one hand, and the potential on the other" (Kemmer 2019). We argue that snow is a source of problems and play in Montreal and that relations with snow constitute intimately woven experiences out of which particular publics emerge (Maeres 2012). We also explore how the affective encounters with snow become more visible as a result of the uncertainty of climate change, the COVID-19 pandemic, and the loss of a knowable winter season.

Hydraulic Hospitality: Waiters as Water Masters in New York City Restaurants *Liviu Chelcea, University of Bucharest*

What would a reconstructed analysis of water hospitality in a piped, urbanized and hydraulically centralized environment look like and attend to? Water hospitality used to figure prominently among ancient hospitality practices, but it has diminished in importance in the ontology of modern piped urban water. Offering water, along with food and wine was taken for granted substance of hospitality, and a pillar of virtue. Invisible in both the anthropology of hospitality and in studies on the proliferation of new forms of water commodification, hydraulic hospitality unfolds and thrives in some sites of the urban piped water infrastructures in the US, yet it is an almost completely ignored ethnographic location. Restaurants in the US are sites where free tap water is abundantly available, a process that sets them apart from restaurants in other countries, where tap is not as automatically, constantly, and unconditionally delivered to patrons. Drawing on fieldwork in New York restaurants and repeated conversations with waiters carried out in 2018, and taking the networked nature of water hospitality in restaurants as an ethnographic entry point, I foreground the figure of waiters as water masters. Waiters' presence transforms the perception of tap water, creates alliances between patrons and various waters available in restaurants, and temporarily suspends diffuse, but widespread fears about water safety. By bringing the ethnographic gaze to bear on hydraulic acts of waiters and hydraulic hospitality, we can get a grounded understanding of the progress and resistance to bottled water commodification, and of networked forms of hospitality.

Becoming-with water: páramo as water factory in infrastructural inflection *Santiago Martínez Medina, Instituto Alexander von Humboldt; Hanne Cottyn, Researcher; Ana María Garrido, Researcher; Joshua Kirshner, University of York*

In this history, water sets a thirsty city in motion. Starting in the 1920s, engineers designed and built the collection, storage, purification, and distribution infrastructures that connect Bogotá, Colombia, with the high mountains surrounding it. The rivers are born on the peaks, in "cool," "desolate," "deserted," and "sad" regions known then as páramos. Following another trajectory, partially connected to the previous one, scientists transformed the notion of páramo in the last century, making it an ecosystem that captures, produces, and regulates water. From wasteland to waterland, páramo becomes a "water factory" and a "strategic ecosystem" that must be conserved. Becoming-with is how

partners are rendered capable, in Haraway and Despret's terms. In this history, páramo is made capable of the city's water infrastructures by becoming a part of them, in a movement that also makes páramo a synonym of water, and water an "ecosystem service" of the páramo: a complex material-semiotic transformation. We think about this convergence based on archival and ethnographic information around the páramos of Chingaza, Sumapaz, and Guerrero, all of them integrated into the Bogotá water supply system. This proposal is part of a project interested in the particular marriage between natural conservation and water in its infrastructural inflection. We suggest that the process we trace enacts páramo as a capitalist nature connected with Bogotá, making impossible other páramo versions: a common Nature, in De la Cadena's terms, with an occulted "infra" partner: capitalism and development for the urban area.

Session Organizer:

Dana Burton, George Washington University

Chair:

Shweta Krishnan, George Washington University

266. Teaching Science and Engineering for Social Justice – III

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Science and engineering education bear significant responsibility in fostering democratic and just technoscientific practice, especially given the complicity of technoscience in several social injustices. For example, AI-based surveillance has reinforced the marginalization of minorities, while the use of toxic chemicals in the electronics industry has caused several worker miscarriages. However, pressured by a market-driven system that prioritizes technical skills, this responsibility is often relegated to ethics or STS courses that are separated from the core science/engineering curriculum. Further, as Dr. Timnit Gebru's recent exit from Google illustrates, the environments of professional technoscience are often themselves averse to critically analyzing issues of social justice and ethics in their practice. Consequently, science and engineering students seldom learn how to engage with social justice as it relates to the subject-matter and methods of technoscience. This is problematic as it can promote agnosticism or even antagonism towards considering the role of technoscience in perpetuating social injustices and inequity. How can we teach science/engineering for social justice in a system that often devalues social justice? In this panel, we invite submissions that critically engage with this question through theoretical and/or practical work. Examples include but are not limited to (re)designing and discussing: • Classroom strategies, courses, or curricula • Digital educational media such as games, simulations, and information visualizations • Policies and power dynamics of the educational system • Personal narratives as educators, administrators, or students as they relate to the challenges of teaching science/engineering for social justice.

Participants:

(Social)justice in engineering education: A magic formula for responsible innovation? *Eunjeong Ma, Pohang University of Science and Technology*

This paper explores a formative hybrid space, in which experts with a wide range of disciplinary matrix in a Kuhnian sense mix together under the same departmental roof of the university to foster innovators in IT-related fields. Based on about 10 years of experience to participate in the process of building the community, the paper follows the trajectory of a contested epistemic and pragmatic space, where the topography of engineering practice and education has to be reconfigured and remapped. In particular, the paper stresses the journey of a STS scholar who has tried to incorporate the notion of justice into the practice of engineering design at the undergraduate level. In a recent decade, the incorporation of non-technical elements such as social science, humanities, arts, and design into core engineering curricula has never been more emphasized in the Korean national context. The government viewed that the unique element of their success should be found in the infusion between

the technical and the social/the humanistic. Since 2011, the South Korean government has funded competitive universities to cultivate global innovators in IT-based industry at the undergraduate and graduate levels. This offered a timely opportunity for the interested academic community to reformulate engineering as the cradle of start-ups derived from innovation. Treating the notion of justice as boundary objects, the paper presents a case study of how this particular sort of innovation community is formed through collaborative efforts between engineers, the industry, the government, and "others."

Lead, Arsenic, and Uranium in Plastic Play Food Toys *Kaleem Ahmid, Northeastern University; Sara Wylie, Northeastern University*

This paper reflects on how to effectively integrate citizen science into the classroom, based on work in a Northeastern University Environmental Health course studying lead exposure in a childcare setting. We describe the process and design of the citizen science study, how it builds on STS work about the importance of praxis to change Environmental Health education (such as in Kenny et al, 2019), and how to combine research and education to improve consumer-safety. We conducted a lead assessment of a daycare using citizen and professional science methods. We identified concerning levels of lead, arsenic and uranium in plastic play food toys (PPFTs). In total we analyzed 220 PPFTs and found: 8.1% (18/220) tested above the lead concentration regulatory thresholds for children's products of 100ppm. 4.2% of the PPFTs tested above the US voluntary standard for arsenic in children's products of 25ppm. This is the first study investigating heavy metals in PPFTs. The results were concerning given that PPFTs are frequently mouthed by children. We discuss how to build collaborative locations-based curriculum that supports novel research findings as well as how to approach novel and challenging experimental findings such as toy chicken-legs that contain uranium and plastic bananas loaded with lead and arsenic. We discuss how to scale class-room based citizen science research to support community-scale interventions such as integrating leaded-toy disposal into existing e-waste recycling programs, as well as legislative measures to strengthen children's protection from heavy metals without shifting the burden onto individual consumers.

Using Role-Play Case Studies to Teach Engineering for Social Justice *Ashish Hingle, George Mason University; Aditya Johri, George Mason University*

Algorithms, embedded as software, are a central component of most services we use across a range of domains. These services, platforms, and devices rely on computing and technology professionals – who work as data scientists, programmers, or artificial intelligence (AI) experts – to meet their intended goals. How do we train future professionals to have an ethical mindset in their understanding, design, and implementation of algorithms and to empower them to be socially just in their design of technology? This was the question that prompted the use of a role-playing case study, which we designed, implemented, and studied in an undergraduate engineering course. We used the Boeing Max 8 flight disaster as the scenario for this case study as it encapsulates how a software algorithm shapes decision-making in a complex scenario. Theoretically, our work is guided by the situated learning paradigm, specifically the need to learn perspectival thinking for decision-making. The ability to make ethical decisions keeping in mind social justice requires the ability to take context into account – to understand not just the immediate (micro) technical but also larger (macro) implications. Findings from the evaluation of the role-play scenario show that students reported a higher engagement and a better understanding of the scenario due to taking on a specific role related to the scenario. Analysis of pre-and post-discussion assignments shows a shift in their perspective of the case, wherein they bring up aspects of social justice in their discussion.

The Case for Teaching Reflexivity in Science and Engineering Education *Aditya Anupam, Georgia Institute Of Technology*

Amidst a rising tide of ethical problems in and by the tech industry, more and more tech employees are speaking up against their companies. Yet, despite some success, many protests and demands still go unheeded. Further, many employees face retaliation by their parent companies, which further perpetuates employee silence on ethical infractions. Given this situation, what role can ethics education play in promoting effective activism? In this paper, I argue that in response to this problem, current ethics education is limited by its emphasis on cultivating awareness and reasoning about ethical situations, and needs to expand its domain to focus more explicitly on ethical action in dialogue with ethical situations. I posit that this requires cultivating in students the virtue of reflexivity, i.e., critically examining the subject of inquiry—their communities of practice and its sociopolitical position—as part of the object of inquiry, i.e., the ethical problem-situation. This is because reflexivity can allow practitioners to better understand their relationship to the problem-situation and the values underlying their work, which are essential for carving out possibilities for action. However, teaching reflexive practice in the classroom is challenging due to students' distance from real world situations. To approach this challenge, I suggest three directions: cultivating student awareness about their position as subjects, providing opportunities to interact with real practitioners, and creating support systems and organizations that educate and mentor students when they become practitioners.

Session Organizer:

Aditya Anupam, Georgia Institute Of Technology

267. Publication Politics I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

This double panel brings together multidisciplinary approaches to investigating the relationships between publication practices and science in diverse national and transnational settings. It puts into conversation research that uses qualitative and quantitative methods and analyzes to investigate the development of the field of Innovation Systems studies, the trajectory of STS social science in Brazil, that articulation of Sustainable Development Goals in Brazilian publications, and the ways citizen science publications represent the motivation for "participation." The panel takes up the question of how scientific publications represent the status of statistical "significance" in Austria, Germany, and Switzerland, as well as critically investigates the role of peer review in STS journals themselves, and the status of the "non-human" in design journals, and even the role of google searchers and hence algorithms in generating results. In so doing, the panel turns a critical eye to both the study of publication in the sciences as well as within STS itself.

Participants:

A biased mind: Significance as a publication booster? *Julia Jerke, University of Zurich; Antonia Velicu, Universität Zürich; Heiko Rauhut, Universität Zürich*

Publishing research results is probably the most fundamental prerequisite of scientific progress. Any finding remaining in the file drawer, independent of its quality, importance or relevance, is in fact meaningless. However, we know from studies on publication bias that what is published is not representative for what is being researched. While the existence of publication bias has been documented across various disciplines, it is widely unexplored how different actors of the scientific system contribute to the problem. We combine quantitative and qualitative elements to provide an in-depth analysis of researchers' perception of significance and how it affects their understanding of research quality. In a quasi-experimental design we confront 15'778 scientists from Austria, Germany and Switzerland with a hypothetical study for which we vary the strength of the statistical results. Across all disciplines, we find

that researchers that are shown a study with statistically significant results rate the methodological approach, the scientific contribution and the publication likelihood substantially higher than those that are shown the identical study but with insignificant results. In a second step, we further analyze the content of 11'250 detailed comments on the study: preliminary results clearly suggest that the (in)significance serves as a strong signal that affects researchers' perception of the study quality. More precisely, the comments reveal that significance seems to matter especially when it is not present. In conclusion, our results demonstrate that the demotion of "failed" research is a widespread and structural problem that has become manifest in the researchers' minds.

Focus on 'successful research' leads to underestimation of research collaboration *J. Hartstein, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW); Bluemel Clemens, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies*

Science and Technology Studies, but also quantitative science studies carry a legacy of research evaluation, represented by concepts as diverse as the h-Index or Altmetrics, focussing on research output. Even research on research collaboration often aims at examining networks of ("successful") knowledge production. Collaboration holds the promise to foster innovation – which is measured in scientometrics in terms of output. We argue, that digital traces of research in progress allow for gaining a more comprehensive picture of the research process and the research collaboration landscape. Failure does not invalidate research. As a complement to studies focussing on output and success, we make collaboration below the threshold of publication visible, including contributions of non-academic staff. For our empirical work, we use data from the version control provider GitHub. We will also elaborate on analytical, methodological and ethical considerations (see also Cosentino et al. 2016, Kalliamvakou et al. 2014): Data traces in digital infrastructures are a certain projection of "reality" onto a special canvas. An obstacle for research on research collaboration as suggested above is the disciplinary bias in coverage in software repositories. Data quality is also an issue as are questions of researcher disambiguation and affiliation. The surveillance aspect of this type of studies is discussed as well as the performativity of our measurements which might lead to unintended consequences.

Mapping the Intellectual Structure and Evolution in Systems of Innovation Research: A Scientometric Approach *Vairaj Arjune, Centre for Studies in Science Policy, Jawaharlal Nehru University; Krishna Tripathi, Centre for Studies in Science policy, Jawaharlal Nehru University, New Delhi*

The present study was conducted to investigate new emerging directions and identify literature by depicting and analysing the historical origins, contemporary research fields and intellectual authors in the domain of Innovation Systems. Using ISI WoS database, we deployed a coherent systematic review of literature using scientometric approaches for delineating the various innovation systems in STS literature and conduct specific analysis of each system. Publications in the WoS database were filtered using the search string "innovat* NEAR/2 syst*" in the publication title for the period 1990-2017. A total of 692 innovation-related publications with contributions from 1171 authors were processed article by article, and as a result 7 innovation clusters were reviewed using highly frequent cited papers. After constructing a co-citation network map to derive characteristics on the theoretical origins and influential publications and authors in IS, we found that 330 (47.68%) of all publications were published in only 12 (5.71%) journals in research areas of business economics, public administration, environmental sciences ecology, geography and science technology. In mapping the evolution of IS, we created a

keyword co-occurrence map which reveals that concepts like "innovation policy" and "innovation system" continues to be dominant research topics in the field of IS, however, emerging topics are moving away from the theories and processes of innovation. The paper aims to be a quick guide to science policy researchers and newcomers to become familiar with this field of study as it examines the theoretical origins and evolution in the field of IS research.

Session Organizer:

Julia Jerke, University of Zurich

268. Aerotechnologies: Air as Elemental Technology - II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

"Objects, processes, or events that in some ways disclose, generate, or intensify the condition of being enveloped by the elemental force of atmospheres," Derek McCormack (2018) proposes, are "atmospheric things." The balloon, for instance, might be construed as a device that not only explicates but also draws force from its immersion in air. We invite papers that contend with aerotechnologies, understood as infrastructures, devices, knowledge systems, and particles that make air as much a technological fact as it is a natural one. What does it mean to study air as elemental technology? How is air — as an element — constitutive, pervasive, and facilitative of emergent kinds of social experiences and relations? How are wind (Howe 2019, Boyer 2019), climate engineering (Furuhata 2019), teargas (Nieuwenhuis 2016), industrial gases (Banken and Stokes 2015), terrariums (Darby 2007), breathing (Braun 2014; Mbembe 2020), as well as other airy matters technologically mediated, rendered, and configured? How does air come to be known or contested through processes of racial, (settler) colonial, and capitalist formations (Flikke 2018, Simmons 2017)? If *techné* denotes the practices of making, we propose that aerotechnologies relate and relay connections between people, non-human actors, epochs, and places, evoking the conference theme that asks what are good (airy) relations? In addition to treating air as technological, we are also interested in papers that explore air as an elemental medium that link different scales of political and social action (Peters 2015, Horn 2018, Choy 2011), especially from perspectives tethered in the global South.

Participants:

Particulate Matter(s): The Scale of the Climate Crisis in the Peruvian Andes *Courtney Evelyn Cecale, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)*

The scale of the climate crisis is made visible through atmospheric particulate matter. Scale is a process of compounding instantiations. It builds in matter, size, scope. Often climate studies and justice work are framed in scale as processes of the aggregate whole of global warming producing localized uneven effects. It is the story of injustice produced in the Global North, with effects in the Global South. This presentation complicates this story: in addition to climate changes from industrial atmospheric pollution from nations like Canada and the United States, actors from those countries, who have expanded operations in places like Peru, export particle producing processes through the expansion of unregulated processes like mining. In the Peruvian Andes, industrially produced particles of soot and black carbon produced by foreign-owned multinational extraction companies coat nearby glaciers, worsening the effects of warming on melt-patterns, with effects so drastic that their disappearance would likely provide decades of more time with these scarce more-than-human beings. In a region with over 70% of the world's tropical glaciers, their disappearance is an existential matter, as it will assuredly lead to the collapse of entire ecosystems, anticipated in just 20 years time. By staying close with the atmospheric particulate matter, this presentation reveals how climate change is produced both as a global aggregate, but also a local and grounded process — both of which reflect and help clarify vectors of power in our global capitalist systems. Further, this work reveals how official global standards and mechanisms for climate accountability, which

measure the production of carbon emissions in a given country, fail to grasp the scalar complexity of atmospheric relationships, made clearer through the atmospheric particulate matter.

Right of Death, Right to Breathe: Tear Gas and the Securitization of Spaces *Jack R Leff, Virginia Tech STS*

Tear gas is a weapon used to manage threats to the neoliberal state and preserve racial capitalism. In effect, the question of who gets gassed can be reframed as: whose breath and, by extension, whose life is seen as valuable? Who, in biopolitical terms, do neoliberal states wish to live and who are they willing to let die? To answer these questions, I contrast the uneven use of tear gas at the January 6th insurrection in Washington, DC with the more frequent gassing of the 2020 Black Lives Matter (BLM) protests in the United States. By reading these two examples of gassing as the management of threatened and racialized spaces, I argue that the relatively lackluster gassing of white nationalists taking the capital betrays the state's willingness to tolerate white supremacy as a useful political tool up until it makes a play for hegemony. Thinking with the conference theme of good relations, I invoke the BLM protests not just as a point of comparison to the capital insurrection as a way to demonstrate racial disparities, but particularly as an example of how activists build counter-public atmospheres. Drawing on my own experiences of being gassed and the tacit knowledge of protest networks, I examine atmospheres of resistance that form in the wake of tear gas's deployment. I argue that the conflict between the noxious aerotechnology of tear gas and the relations of care that BLM protesters develop reveals how activists effectively construct counter-publics to the state's securitization of air.

Variations on Aeolian Dynamics: For Contained Winds *Joel Ong, York University*

In the Fall of 2020, a small team entered the WindEEE Hexagonal Dome at Western University to explore the interactions of a dancer with and within a simulated tornado. Our goal was to engage creatively with a force of nature distilled to movement and vorticity through precise engineering, and to document moments of connection in a controlled environment. Due to Covid, itself a manifestation of the un-containable aspects of aerodynamics, this project pivoted to an online presentation, allowing digital media to become the mode of visualizing the effects of the wind on the body. In this case, the body was presented, as philosopher of architecture Greg Lynn would describe, as a diagram of 'gradient forces' through with a continuum of wind was expressed. In stark contrast to the containment of the wind within highly specialized facilities of wind modelling and simulation, the project speaks to the 'commonwealth' of air as an opening of both physical architectures to external atmospheres, but also to the metaphorical opening of in vitro and in silico spaces (lab and screen) to artistic expression and collaboration. Therefore, this paper is a review of the artist's interventions and immersions within the WindEEE dome, the nature of the project's truncation and pivot due to Covid restrictions, the limitations of artistic-scientific discourse/motivations, and the lingering questions around translation. The project will be framed in 4 'études' or studies (2 of which are currently on show at the Macintosh Gallery in Western) around artistic research on contained winds.

Session Organizer:

Boyd Ruamcharoen, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Chair:

Jia Hui Lee, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Discussant:

Courtney Evelyn Cecale, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)

269. Toxic Entanglements: acting on slow, invisible, and emerging realities - II: Risky Engagements

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

Entangled practices: Seeking good relations between harm reduction and poly-drug use *Hayley Murray*

Poly-drug use appears firmly and visible within the landscape of young people's drug use lives. This experimentation with different psychoactive chemicals has the potential for both increasing pleasure and creating invisible harms. Young people who engage in poly-drug use are conducting ongoing experiments with the multiple illicit and licit substances that become entangled inside the body. Their practices of tinkering with dosages, substances, and settings are done in the hopes of reducing drug-related harm while maximizing physical and social pleasure. Such practices, that fall under a concept that we refer to as 'harm reduction from below' are explored via tracing the drug use trajectories of a subset of young British recreational poly-drug users and their complex relationship with three popular drugs: MDMA/ecstasy, cocaine, and alcohol. The motivation behind this exploration of good relations of these drugs is to lessen the harms brought on by their drug use. However, with the perceived safer choice of one substance over another, we see the emergence of invisible, unexpected harms and negative consequences. A new understanding of the motivations behind these practices requires our attention. Ultimately, this pathway analysis demonstrates that the harm reduction from below practices can actually produce more damaging, more long-term negative effects on these young people within the backdrop of a binge-drinking culture. In the end, we call upon institutions and governments to provide visible harm reduction from above on the risk of this common co-consumption to bring balance to harm reduction.

Exploring technomolecular governance: actors and interests in microscopic urban metabolic flows *Raul Acosta, Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität Munich*

Cities concentrate consumption of products and uses of materials laden with chemicals whose combined effects remain elusive. In this paper, I argue that there is a growing need for good technomolecular governance in order to map and oversee the production, uses, and repercussions of microscopic elements. I also consider that it is particularly useful to conceptualize these particles as urban metabolic flows, in order to grasp the dynamic character of their presence and effects. Some data-driven policies are in place to study specific aspects of such flows, like the scanning wastewater epidemiology or atmospheric sampling. But there is as of yet no effort to visualize and analyze the complex combinations that human and other-than-human life forms are exposed to. This in turn may help shape specific studies of certain composites, or lead to renewed thinking of regulations and infrastructures. This reflection is part of a larger project with which I plan to carry out an anthropological ethnographic study of urban metabolic flows in Mexico. The project is framed within the emerging chemo-ethnography field, that approaches environmental concerns as entangled with health, of the sort proposed by the one health and the planetary health research agendas. It seeks to explore ideas of good governance where novel forms of stakeholder engagement may occur. Scientists and civil society organizations have often sought to address risks of toxic environments by focusing on single threats as sources of illness or risk. Exploring the viability of mechanisms of technomolecular governance may help shape innovative ways to address toxic entanglements.

Narrating Toxic Stress: Cortisol and Oxytocin as Epigenetic Objects *Andie Thompson, University of Amsterdam - AISSR*

Chemical toxicity is often narrated in biomedical discourses as originating from external exposures, locating chemicals spatially and in proximity to bodies, in the air, the water, the food consumed, or applied to the skin. Recent research into the long

term health effects of toxic stress disrupts the idea that health concerns related to toxicity are matters of material exposure only and opens a scientific interest in understanding the interconnections between environmental factors that prefigure bodies endogenous chemical pathways and health outcomes. Toxic stress as a concept describes fluidity between underlying physiology and lived-experiences, indexing interpersonal relationships, societal structures, and temporalities of exposures that predetermine biological generations in advance as loci of formative exposures. Drawing on a remote ethnography of epigenetics and maternal health, I highlight the research of two scientists in Portland, Oregon working to narrate the effects of toxic stress in maternal and infant bodies by following the overabundance and under absorption of endogenously produced chemicals, oxytocin and cortisol. I analyze how the methods used by scientists in charting pathways between stress exposures and neurophysiological outcomes, presents a case to consider the entanglements of slow-toxicity as a problem of “heterogeneous responsiveness” – the different ways bodies are sensitized to respond to environmental features. Through this narration of toxic stress, the scientists I am working with offer epigenetic models that capture the ways underlying physiology interacts with social structures and biological characteristics to shape future health. In this paper, I explore what these models and the scientist’s intention behind them can add to the conversation of reproductive justice and inform the design of maternal health interventions.

The Everyday Life Of ‘Risk’ : Making Sense Of ‘Safety’ Against The Backdrop Of Field Encounters *Abhigya Abhigya, Indian Institute of Technology Delhi,*

Agricultural pesticides, their physical and chemical properties, and the health and environmental effects associated with their use, stimulate a range of debates which take place in different social, political and institutional contexts. Pesticides have pathways through social, political and institutional systems which lead them into the daily lives of farmers. This paper traces these trails through the everyday encounters and negotiations of pesticide users with these chemicals, in western Uttar Pradesh region in India, the heartland of the green revolution, and gauge how they are tied to the questions of knowledge and regulation. It explores how pesticide use practices in the cultivation of Basmati Rice varieties in the region are shaped by interactions between various set of actors across the network of rice cultivation and its export. The paper presents a close view of these interactions and draws on STS theories of risk, uncertainty, co-production of knowledge and regulatory sciences to help explicate the various ways in which knowledge is constructed around the risk, safety, use and chronic health effects of pesticides. The discussion is built upon perspectives gained through in-depth interviews with agricultural scientists, representatives from the pesticide industry, farmers, farm labourers and pesticide retailers in the aforementioned region.

Canary Science in the Mineshaft of the Anthropocene: From Risk to Vulnerability *Liza Grandia, University of California-Davis*

Alongside the melting of glaciers, human bodies warn of another “anthropogenic” planetary crisis of ubiquitous toxicity. Like climate change, this was a chronicle foretold. Many of the 1970s disasters (Three Mile Island, Love Canal, Cuyahoga, etc.) that inspired the passage of major environmental legislation also stimulated academic interest in technological hazards. The experts who initially dominated this field assumed that laboratory scientists understood the “real” objective risk, while the “perceived” views of the public were subjective, uninformed, false, illusory, or irrational. Then the risk experts themselves fell ill. Albeit not ordinary environmental justice subjects, I review how EPA scientists, college professors, lawyers, medical doctors, military officers, and even toxicologists themselves were struck with a rash of idiopathic environmental illnesses and cancer.

Vindicating the popular epidemiology of these “canaries in the mineshaft,” a new wave of environmental health scientists are rethinking the hallmarks of cancer etiology, the exposome, and the cumulative, collective toll of low-dose exposures. Beyond democratic values of “citizen science,” I make a case for the extra-sensory value of “canary science” as a symbol of our common vulnerability in a toxic anthropocene. If managerial “risk” was the keyword of the profiteering twentieth century, a sense of shared vulnerability in the coronavirus era might usher the transitions needed to survive our plural petrochemical-driven planetary crises.

Session Organizer:
Anita Hardon

270. Total Institutions: Technosciences of Care and Control I

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Erving Goffman (1961) called both prisons and psychiatric wards “total institutions,” gesturing to the intertwined nature of care, capture, and control in efforts to manage deviance of the soul, psyche, or self. This panel investigates institutions and techniques of mental health care in the Global North, South, and colonial contexts, grappling with the criminological, forensic, pastoral and penal impulses of the psy-disciplines. Building from the work of feminist science and technology studies, abolitionist scholarship (Wang 2018), studies of racial capitalism (Robinson 1983), and historical and sociological studies of psychiatry, social services, and the prison industrial complex (Roberts 2001, Metz 2010, Ryan Hatch 2019, Raz 2020, Smith 2020), panelists will explore the connective tissue between the prison and the asylum, probing the practices, histories, expertise and apparatuses within the mental health care professions and other social services (from psychiatry, psychology, psychotherapy, and beyond) that knit together the carceral with the biomedical.

Participants:

Care in the “Automatic Environment”: Autism and the Origins of Data Behaviorism *Jeff Nagy, Dept. Communication, Stanford University*

An electric train, a trained pigeon, a kaleidoscope, a phonograph, a telephone, a television, and an eight-column candy vending machine: in 1960, all of these were present at the birth of one of the most well-established autism therapy paradigms. Notable for their absence were human caregivers or psychiatrists, hidden from view by a one-way screen while their experiments with autistic children proceeded without intervention, “programmed and recorded automatically” through “relay, electronic devices, and electrical recorders” (Ferster and DeMyer, 1961). This paper examines the entangled histories of behaviorist research and autism treatment in the middle of the twentieth century. In part, I ask how psychiatric care shifted as it became ambient, displaced from human others onto an “automatic,” “artificial,” or “prosthetic” environment, and how that shift shaped a longer lineage of autism treatment paradigms in prosthetic environments that also functioned as total panopticons. But I also argue that these histories can shed new light on the intertwined surveillance and service that is a core characteristic of surveillance capitalism (Zuboff, 2018) by revealing part of the history of data behaviorism (Rouvroy, 2012), an epistemology tacitly adopted by big data mining. Drawing on scholarship in disability studies and the work of autistic scholars in particular, I argue that mid-century behaviorist researchers’ framing of the subjects under their care – as, simultaneously, raw material for conditioning in automatic environments, and as a human laboratory technology that made new psychological knowledge possible – echoes through the kinds of subjectivities that surveillance capitalism creates and cares for.

“Angela’s Psych Squad”: Black Psychology against the Carceral State in the 1970s *Michael Pettit, York University*

This paper examines the forensic psychology advanced by

affiliates of the Westside Community Mental Health Center in 1970s. Westside served as the organizational hub for the nascent Association for Black Psychologists and its efforts to disrupt the American carceral state. California, more so than any other state in the country, was seduced by the dream of human improvement through therapeutic interventions in schools and prisons intended to correct the wayward deviant. The Westside psychologists revealed the lie behind this dream, showing it as a eugenic nightmare with a price unequally extracted from Black lives. Inspired by the diagnoses advanced by the Black Panther Party, the Westside psychologists sought to dismantle the interlinked disciplinary apparatus which disproportionately surveyed, tracked, and confined young Black men. They mounted a legal challenge to the use standardized intelligence testing to sort Black children in California schools. They consulted on the voir dire process in the highly politicized Angela Davis trial to minimize the presence of racially prejudiced jurors. They offered expert testimony on the psychological effects of solitary confinement on behalf of prison activists. At the heart of their interventions lay a recasting of “bias” as a concept by deliberately co-mingling the term’s statistical and sociological meanings. The paper draws on the extensive press coverage to examine these psychologists’ self-fashioning as clinicians deploying their intersubjective judgment under circumstances where they were not perceived as reliable witnesses. Responses from the American Psychological Association to these efforts curtailed the radical potentiality of what forensic psychology could become.

Modeling/Treating Addiction: Race, Psyche & The Politics Of Care *Chad Valasek, University of California at San Diego*

Sitting at the crossroads of critical race studies and disability studies, my project tracks the development of different models of behavioral treatments in relation to addiction and carcerality from the 1960s to today with a focus on US psychology and psychiatry. In particular, I explore the tensions between biology, culture, and individual willpower in models of addiction within treatment centers, asylums, and prisons. Following the behavioral experiments of the early and mid 20th century, late 20th century models tried to grapple with loss of self-control. Here I track the development of hyperbolic discount rates and present-bias in the behavioral sciences, which correlated impulsivity with addiction, criminality, low IQ, and poverty. However, in arguing against the implicit race science of the 1970s-1990s, Black psychologists developed counter models that focused on cultural factors rather than individual behavior alone. Recent developments in addiction treatments within psychiatric and carceral institutions have attempted to include more cognitive-behavioral and mindfulness programs. Although such programs do not exclude the fact that others still receive chemical constraint treatments. Following Ryan (2019) and Kerrison (2017), I examine the differences of treatments to certain groups, particularly Black and disabled populations, over time. While paying attention to the racism embedded in the history of incarceration, my project seeks to differentiate the logics of various treatments and the tension between care and punishment in these cases. The findings from this history may then lead to conceptualizing new abolitionist possibilities of treatment and care outside of carceral logics.

The Spillover: A Cultural History of Network Science *Olivia Banner, University of Texas at Dallas*

This paper excavates the origins of network science in 1930s research at Sing Sing Prison and the New York State Training School for Girls. J. L. Moreno, founder of sociometry and group psychodrama, conducted research on group relations at these prisons, using network graphs to plot attractions and repulsions among the incarcerated and publishing his work in papers and reports in the 1930s up through the 1950s, when he updated those network graphs for scalability. In his work, Moreno justified the network graph as a method for creating harmonious “planned communities,” and he advocated the therapeutic practice he

created, spontaneity training, for rehabilitating social deviants. Ella Fitzgerald was one of the “wayward girls” imprisoned at Hudson for being “ungovernable.” Fitzgerald, like others at Hudson, escaped; decades later, a former superintendent reported that, once famous, Fitzgerald refused invitations to visit the school, because she had been beaten by the male guards. Although Moreno’s work discusses runaways, race, and queer attractions, the gendered and racialized violence fueling their fugitivity did not factor into Moreno’s conclusions, even as the network graphs were designed specifically to “map” currents of fugitivity. That is, Moreno’s network visualizations diagrammed, in order to capture, moments of flight from anti-queer, anti-Blackness. I explore what it means that a core visualization method in network science emerged from a carcerality premised on containment of “the spillover” — queerness, Blackness — that reformers identified as their rehabilitative mission.

Session Organizer:

Beth Semel, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Chair:

Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley

271. Composting Feminisms and Environmental Humanities Panel - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Composting, as a feminist practice, has been taken up by an open, cross-institutional, trans-disciplinary reading and research group exploring the traces, legacies and relations between inclusive feminisms and broad Environmental Humanities over the last six years. The Composting Feminisms and Environmental Humanities group wishes to connect with composting kin around the world through this second open panel at 4S. At 4S 2018 we held a full day of interconnecting open discussions examining the transnational intersections between new environmentalisms and feminist STS. Forming good relations and worlding better worlds informs all of our endeavors, making 4S 2020 an ideal venue for Composting. The Composting group exists because although we cannot envision feminisms without attending to queer, Indigenous, anti-racist, anticolonial, crip, and other intersectional perspectives, often environmental thought neglects these questions. How might we attune ourselves to the ways in which new ideas are indebted to writings, readings and practices that have come before? How are feminist genealogies composted in and through the Environmental Humanities? What ethics of care and responsibility emerge from these ideas? What is yet to be added to the compost pile? We encourage submissions that continue the process of breaking down matters to re-emerge as new matters. Together we attune ourselves to the good (and fraught) relations that already exist and are yet to be formed between these modes of knowing.

Participants:

Soft Survival: Foraging Feminisms *Maya S Livio, University of Colorado / Media Archaeology Lab*

This hybrid talk/performance will present one component of 'Soft Survival', an ongoing research-creation experiment in developing alternatives to survivalist conceptions of impending emergency. While emergency is often framed as a future, doomsday scenario, 'Soft Survival' insists on an ongoing emergency, disproportionately affecting marginalized peoples. The project weaves feminist STS, environmental humanities, and adapted “prepping” practices to compost how surviving and thriving can be constructed differently—as connection with, rather than domination, over nature, and as a process in which necessities for living are viewed as shareable and abundant rather than individual and scarce. The talk will center specifically on foraging practices, taking into consideration how the ethics of food and embodied foraging knowledges materialize theory, and sharing both findings and recipes.

An Ode to Jodi Doering *Jennifer Loureide Biddle, National Institute of Experimental Art UNSW Art & Design*
Jodi Doering, South Dakota Registered Nurse, garnered

international attention for tweeting distress at the number of ER patients in her care dying from Covid-19: 'This can't be happening. It's not real'. This creative non-fiction is an experiment in ethnography; an attestation to a front-line predicament and the impossible imperative of paying attention, of care, of survival, in this year of the daily case-count, fake news, too-much-information. Following Susan Briante (and as she does, the work of Claudia Ranken, Molten and Harney, Roberto Tejada) I want to explore the role of writing in this context. To pay homage to Jodi Doering in ways that move beyond look at her witnessing, or look at me and my witnessing, while holding on to the critical acts of call-out, embodied intervention and the authoring of responsibility in the concrete and micro-attentive ways that ethnographic writing enables. I am interested in writing as radical empiricism. How to document violence built upon the bodies of others and what terms responsibility can take in what, and who, counts in the racialized, gendered, class-ed terms that Jodi's act presents. What are differences in care, the differential calls and heeding of citizenship(s); who dies, who lives, who pays for what debt? What are the limits and demands of new composting(s) of kin and cultivations of ethical ecologies, when distance may be the most responsible way to engage and yet is bound to intractable inequities, distributions, hierarchies – disposable, killable, statistical bodies– in contrast to those who might stand to witness.

Compost poetics: The fertile discord between queer and feminist epistemologies *Rebecca Ream*

Donna Haraway really revels in the practice of shredding the skin of the self-contained figure of Man. A still potent symbol of masculine human Western supremacy, often illustrated by the Vitruvian Man or the Man of Perfect proportions, Haraway's composting offers a feminist and queer response to this problematic Western ontology. However, queer and feminist epistemologies do not always play well together even if they are both means of challenging heteronormativity in patriarchal and misogynistic societies (Showden, 2012). Whilst the former tends to disrupt norms and 'naturalisms', the latter potentially validates 'norms' like heterosexual relationships and heteronormative reproduction when arguing the case for women's emancipation (Showden, 2012). As someone with a lively queer sensibility (Taylor, 2013), Haraway herself does not like the concept of 'reproduction' because of the way it claims and tries to duplicate what was there before, thus reinscribing Western ideas of 'production' — a fertile contribution to the field of STS. I myself am less wary of the concept of reproduction. Does this, I ask myself, betray my otherwise devotion to the philosopher? To work through these personal and political tensions — including Haraway's own queer feminism — I use critical autoethnography and the poetics of compost to show how queer and feminist epistemologies discordantly make worlds together. Such poetic rendering exposes me as a promiscuous composter and queerer of STS who strays from Haraway and then re-turns (to) the pile once again to make odd kin (Haraway, 2016) with her.

The Armidale Climate and Health Project: Composting and Weathering as Community Action Research *Ethic Jennifer Mae Hamilton, University of New England; Sujata Allan, Armajun Aboriginal Health Service*

This paper will report on the Armidale Climate and Health Project currently happening in my hometown of Armidale NSW. The project is guided by the concepts composting / weathering which centre both inclusive feminist and environmental concerns. The project seeks to centre indigenous knowledge and health in decolonising ways, and the practical experience of enacting this project will be reflected on in this presentation. The project includes six workshops and a festival. Each workshop has been designed to capture the ethical orientations of composting and weathering in non-dogmatic ways. The themes of the workshops are: legal property access for First Nations, trauma

and healing, water, student activism, food justice and being an anti-colonial and environmentally focussed medical professional. The project website is <http://www.armidaleclimateandhealth.com.au> and will be active throughout 2021.

Session Organizer:

Lindsay Kelley, UNSW Art & Design

Chair:

Lindsay Kelley, UNSW Art & Design

272. Screenings

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: *Exhibition - Screenings*

Screenings

Participant:

Screenings *Patrick Keilty, University of Toronto*

Screenings

Session Organizer:

Patrick Keilty, University of Toronto

273. Making and Doing Exhibition - 2

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: *Making and Doing - 2*

Making and Doing Exhibition - 2

Participant:

Making and Doing Exhibition - 2 *Hélène Mialet, York University STS*

Making and Doing Exhibition - 2

Session Organizer:

Hélène Mialet, York University STS

FRIDAY, OCTOBER, 8

274. Contemplating Models and Methods for Futures in-the-making - II

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Predicting and planning for the future is an inherently uncertain exercise. In the midst of unfolding health and environmental crises, forecasting the implications of different types of interventions is important but precarious. With exhortations from governments to 'flatten the curve,' simulation modelling has recently gained prominence in public consciousness as a potent tool informing COVID policies. The simplicity of the models stands in stark contrast to the complexity of the challenges at hand. This panel explores ways for STS to interpret and inform debates around 'modelling' practice and public understandings of models for the future. How and why are simulation models so seductive? How are models shaping concepts of 'self' and 'future'? What kinds of knowledges and assumptions are built into these speculative exercises and what (or who) is left out? Can models help build 'good relations' between governments and citizens, or between diverse stakeholders approaching complex problems? The panel invites papers that engage with critical approaches to modelling practice and models as symbols circulating in complex systems. We also encourage papers that explore alternative methods for engaging in forecasting and scenario building that may better be able to encompass complex intervention dynamics and marginalized futures.

Participants:

"A Life Cut Short:" Life Expectancy Models During The COVID-19 Pandemic *Kristin Gupta, Rice University, Department of Anthropology*

The idea that humans will live for a particular amount of time is undergoing intense transformation in the United States, especially in the wake of the COVID-19 pandemic. Over the past

century, the dominant American ideal of what constitutes a good death has primarily become a peaceful one that happens in old age—an imaginary that has generally become only more achievable as lifespans have more than doubled since the 1800s. However, in a time when medical and mortuary facilities have been overwhelmed with more than 525,000 dead, the assumption that most will live to their eighties or beyond has become less tenable. In particular, a growing coalition of American end-of-life (EOL) doulas have increasingly taken up contemporary cultural anxieties about mortality and the future in their deathcare practices like virtual advanced directives workshops. Aiming to interrogate logics of progress and “breathless futurology” (Harrington et al. 2006) of biotechnologies like cryogenics and anti-aging innovations, doulas’ project is one that increasingly questions one of the most central assumptions of contemporary life in the global North: living a long life. This paper will ethnographically trace how their work reorients the self towards death and the future, opening up broader conversations about histories of human lifespans and their relations to quantification, abstraction, and risk. How are models of the future like life expectancy practiced and lived with? How do they shape perceptions and interpretation of the world around us? To what extent have these orientations changed in a time of mass death?

Relational Practices and Methods for Participatory Ecological Ethnography *Kara E. Miller, California State University, Long Beach*

This talk explores ethnographic approaches and methodologies utilized for examining toxicity and cultural ecologies in Long Beach, CA. Industrial landscapes, including ports and diesel commerce zones, oil drilling, with vast chemical pollutants, have toxic effects on surrounding neighborhoods. As an anthropologist, my work aims to decenter hegemonic notions of science, celebrate local ecological knowledge production, and utilize relational methods of engagement to facilitate meaning-making in community health research. Good relations, whether in the ethnographic encounter or in industry’s interface with local environments, are based in mutuality, responsibility, and sustainability. This paper discusses relational, collaborative, and participatory methods aimed to empower local communities with outreach information as well as research tools for monitoring their own environmental health and toxicity. This work highlights collaborative and community-based efforts to study, manage, or mitigate hazardous environmental effects, including participatory action research (PAR), in order to make for better relationships between industry, technology, and community. For communities of color whose vulnerabilities are compounded by myriad issues of environmental racism and ecological injustices, methods to measure geopolitical inequalities of pathological exposure can lead the way to better policies for healthy community development, better chemical policies, informed ethics for new ecological well-being, or policies that bridge law-makers or other stakeholders with community members. Using critical ecological approaches, Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK), and community science research projects, this work has community members explore and survey toxic exposures as a means of relating with the environment, as well as attuning to what sovereign emplacements of the future might necessitate.

The Decision to Modelize: Microsimulation Tools Planning the Future of Belgian Social Policies *Isalyne Stassart, Université de Liège / Institut Wallon de l'évaluation, de la prospective et de la statistique*

Throughout the Belgian federalization process, federated entities (communities and regions) have been using model-based expertise to anticipate the reception of social policies in dramatically asymmetrical fashions, ranging from evaluation regarding poverty reducing indicators to overarching pursuit of future budgetary equilibrium. Following the predicting activities focused on the impacts of future shifts in child benefits policies,

one can see that microsimulation models are now broadly used. It appears that the use of such tools started at the academic level, before spreading to governments and administrations through a growing knowledge network – and now constitute an unavoidable stage in some entities. Other entities are less prone to microsimulation, but either ways, public decisions are always marked by some kind of model. The growing importance of such practices raise a lot of questions in terms of data collection, model design trust in public decision, all of which causes new domains of governmentality (FALLON & STASSART, forthcoming). Studying both domestic models and the EUROMOD model (the largest model in Europe), our contribution will intend to “open the box” (THOREAU & LAURENT, 2020) of a number a modelling tools; trace their origin and datasets; and question their new role as near-infrastructures restricting forecasting to a specific set of indicators and shaping future expertise in academia, government and general population. Our observations will be based on more than sixty in-depth interviews with practitioners of models; a EUROMOD-training; and an ethnographic stay in one of the two central research centers specialized in microsimulation in Belgium.

The Economy of Predictive Knowledge. Public Investments and Private Development of Software Tools to Predict Chemical Risks *David Demortain, INRAE, LISIS*

How does it matter that models and IT tools for prediction and simulation are developed by private actors, when these models and tools are aimed to help regulatory authorities predict and protect against hazards? The public regulation of the chemical industry rests on the use of IT tools that were developed to predict the most common toxicities associated with various families of molecules. Public regulatory authorities and chemical firms have a joint interest in using such predictive tools, namely the fact that these tools reduce the amount of animal experimentation to perform before allowing chemicals on the market, making it less time consuming, costly, but also more ethical. Of all of the tools used, some are more strictly speaking “predictive”: they allow for simulating highly specific, quantitative models, to numerically determine the toxicity of new molecules. Publicly-developed tools are of a different sort: they are more of a screening platform, allowing to compare data concerning series of molecules, to produce a hypothesis about the likelihood that a newly developed molecule, comparable to past ones, develop one sort of toxicity or another. In other words, commercial tools seem to respond to the wishes of the chemical industry to reach a high level of precision, to adjust (and minimize) regulatory intervention on their products. Publicly-developed tools aim less for precision, but more for reliable and credible simulations, allowing to take firm, non-contestable decisions. Drawing on these observations about differing epistemologies underlying public or private tools, this paper will explore what one may call the political economy of prediction, verifying if the broader political economy of chemicals regulation, said to be one of industry dominance, reflects in dominant ways of predicting.

Session Organizer:

Victoria Loblay, Menzies Centre for Health Policy, The Australian Prevention Partnership Centre

275. Dis/connected – Reassembling security through digital data practices

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Digital data practices and related algorithmic forms of regulation are reshaping security politics (Aradau 2017; Bellanova and de Goede 2020). From the molecular to the planetary, from the individual body to the Earth system, data increasingly becomes the primary means of self-preservation. This panel furthers the debate on the way in which security politics are reassembled through data practices. Critical works on dataveillance often

draw on macro-level analytics, including Foucault's dispositif or Deleuze's societies of control. While this critique is important, it assumes that "big data" works. It risks reproducing the imaginary of the power of big data analytics, overlooking their failures and fragilities. This panel contributes to the debate on big data and surveillance in STS by bringing it into dialogue with Critical Security Studies (Bellanova et al. 2020).

Acknowledging the multiple worlds enacted in digital data practices, the panel develops a critique of such worlds from within. The contributions focus on the concrete 'doings' of digital data in security practices and show how security is becoming-with data analysis (cf. Kaufmann 2020). Digital data are not only a means of control, they are also changing how security operates: new actors and sites of security emerge, including social media and online platforms. Security logics are changing, too, e.g. through algorithmic regulation, digital databases, and machine vision. The papers trace new relations between heterogeneous actors and the production of novel subject positions, including "coder soldiers" or "digital visual subjects". Finally, they theorize failure as an inherent feature of data-driven security operations.

Participants:

Unknowns, time pressures, business continuities: The fragility of fingerprint matching in EU databases *Matthias Leese, ETH Zurich*

European databases for security, migration, and border management are largely predicated on the inscription of biometric data (fingerprints, palmmarks, facial images, DNA) and algorithmic matching capacities that allow for queries to confirm identities (1:1 search) or identify unknown persons (1:n search). Whereas biometrics are in public communications often represented as straightforward and sure-fire solution that are capable of producing 'truthful' knowledge, empirical analysis reveals the messy and multiple socio-technical relations of biometric matching. This paper analyzes the Automated Fingerprint Identification Systems (AFIS) in two European databases for security, migration, and border management (the Schengen Information System and the Visa Information System) as well as the 'shared biometric matching service' of the interoperability framework that cuts across these and other systems. The analysis draws attention to how the matching of fingerprints is shaped by contingencies in the creation of biometric templates (e.g., low quality scans, partial prints, latent prints), the operational requirements of law enforcement and border control (e.g., speed, reliability), and connections with already existing systems and infrastructures. In doing so, the paper highlights how the matching of fingerprints requires continuous translation activities among a fragmented network of human and non-human elements and draws out the fragile foundations of knowledge and power in the government of security, migration, and borders.

Bringing data to the front: Bringing data to the front: Soldier-coders, subjects and remoteness in "prototype warfare" *Marijn Hoijsink*

This paper uncovers the role of experimental data collection and experimental learning on and beyond the battlefield. While the military has a long history of engaging in experimental learning as part of exercises, gaming and scenario planning, what is different in today's context of what I call "prototype warfare" is how experimental learning is supposed to happen in real-time – in battle or near the edge of battle – as well as on a constant basis. In this context, the constant collection of data from multiple sources is not only used to track and target populations, but also to increase learning or optimize military operations in the broadest sense. A key figure who embodies these developments is the "soldier coder", a new type of soldier, trained in software development and data science who can work and rework algorithms on, or very near, the frontlines of the battlefield. In this paper, I rely on interviews with soldier coders and the study of training manuals and other defense materials to draw out the work of writing code, building machine learning

layers and preparing datasets on or near the frontline. I argue that the work of the soldier coder contributes to the blurring of boundaries between military and civilian assets and targets and further complicates questions of where the battlefield begins and ends. That is, in the work of the soldier coder, military intervention becomes itself reconfigured – and justified – as a learning experience and opportunity for data collection.

Hashes to Hashes. Private Algorithmic Regulation as Excommunication *Rocco Bellanova, UVA*

Social media are sites of security practice. The diffusion of online terrorist content is a concern for public authorities and private companies, and proposals for supranational regulation and increasing use of AI tools are multiplying. However, there are security technologies already in place and they deserve critical attention. This paper unpacks the security and international politics of a privately managed system of algorithmic regulation – the Hash Database. Used and governed by members of the Global Internet Forum to Counter Terrorism, it is behind the majority of content removals. This database stores strings of characters – "hashes" – that moderation services algorithmically extract from those digital objects identified as harmful content. Big Tech companies (Facebook, Microsoft, Twitter, Google...) use this hash-algorithm on all digital objects that users upload on their platforms. In case of match with hashes stored in the database, digital objects are not published or are immediately removed – in principle without having to 'look' at their content. This contribution explores this practice through the lens of "excommunication," bringing new media studies to bear on CSS literature on lists and their politics (de Goede et al. 2016). Indeed, excommunication is 'a question of community, belonging, and judgment before the law' (Galloway et al. 2014, 15). Focusing on the Hash Database's functionalities, frictions and institutionalization, the paper casts a light on lesser studied facets of commercial security. Notably, it questions how Big Tech algorithmic regulation performs the international, and explores how IT companies become crucial players in the field of counterterrorism.

Machine vision, security knowledge, and the parameters of assembled subjectivity *Rune Saugmann, Tampere University*

How are digital images turned into security knowledge, and to which effects? For a long time, military techno-vision was related to the optical qualities of the human eye. It was either about enhancing the natural human eye, seeing further, seeing in less light, seeing from different locations, or about mimicking the human eye, creating spatial awareness and navigation capabilities from the singular point of the eye/camera. In today's 'sensor society', seeing is not the problem for security bureaucracies, understanding is. The knowledge problem is about the mind rather than the eye, to use the anthropomorphic language that dominates high-tech discourse, not about overcoming invisibility but rather about making sense of a flood of opaque images. This challenge has seen military bureaucracies delegating image interpretation to artificial intelligence, in some ways mimicking and increasingly merging with the ways in which social media platforms sort the millions of images they handle. I explore current machine vision technologies and the ways in which social media platforms handle images, and ask what these different ways of handling digital images can tell about our understanding of algorithmic understanding in security agency, and about how digital visual subjects are made and become available for computational security politics and governance.

Governing digital Gaia: EU Copernicus and the socio-technical imaginary of geospatial big data *Delf Rothe, Institute for Peace Research and Security Policy at the University of Hamburg*

The Anthropocene is a time of increasing risk and uncertainty – at least for many people on this planet. For others, it represents a business opportunity. Accelerating climate change displaces and

mobilizes people, species, molecules and matter across the globe. The increasingly unruly planet becomes a gigantic data machine. At the same time, the “creative destruction” of natural disasters opens up exceptional spaces, in which the application of new technologies and forms of governance can be tested. The recent trend of applying geospatial technologies, big data and AI in the fields of humanitarian governance, climate adaptation or disaster management testifies to this development. The proposed paper asks for the political implications of this trend and critically discusses its underlying sociotechnical imaginary around the idea of a digital twin Earth – a digital data double of the planet based on the combination of geospatial big data and advanced computer modeling. The paper traces the novel actor-networks assembled around the twin Earth imaginary – including international organizations such as UNDP, philanthropists and tech startups, defense businesses and, government programs like the EU’s Earth Observation Program Copernicus. It asks how the imaginary of the twin Earth circulates through these networks and discusses how it changes authority and power in the governance of environmental risks. Empirically, the paper draws on 40 research interviews with members of this emerging community as well as field research conducted at political conventions, including the European Space Week or the Big Data from Space convention.

Session Organizer:

Delf Rothe, Institute for Peace Research and Security Policy at the University of Hamburg

Chair:

Nina Klimburg Witjes, Vienna University

Discussant:

Mareile Kaufmann, Universitetet i Oslo

276. **Aspiring Societal Impact. The Epistemological Politics of Interventionist Research in STS - III**

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Participants:

Doing Conceptual Multiplicity: Working cosmologies together and separately in northern Australia *Michaela Spencer, Charles Darwin University; Yasunori Hayashi, Charles Darwin University; Leonie Norrington, Charles Darwin University; Christine Tarbutt-Buckley, Charles Darwin University; Simon West, Charles Darwin University*

At the 4S/EASST conference in 2020, this group presented a Making and Doing exhibition called ‘Making and Doing TopEndSTS – on country (and online)?’ That presentation took the form of a website, and displayed a number of collaborative research projects working at the intersection of Indigenous and other academic traditions. Read together, this collaborative initiative explored what it means to do research and differing epistemics together in ways that entwines technologies of representation and people in generative ways. In revisiting this collaborative work again in 2021, we extend this initial exploration. Now, we focus up tensions between collaborative project research in northern Australia carried out as practical and interventionary, and the efforts needed to ensure the work can retain the epistemic flexibility to ‘work different cosmologies together and separately’, as a key element of generative research work. In presenting stories from our respective research sites, we suggest that beginning with recognising the significance of negotiating conceptual multiplicity, offers one way to work with an often-assumed contradiction between epistemically valid research and generative intervention.

Navigating the feminist politics of inclusion in sport *Madeleine Pape, Northwestern University*

In recent years, the regulation of female athlete eligibility has emerged as one of the most divisive public issues facing

international sport. Such debates frequently pit the interests and dreams of women athletes against those of transgender women and women with high testosterone. For many advocates of women’s sport, the scientific case is clear: only those women who align with normative notions of the female body ought to be allowed to compete in women’s sport, with little room for discussing the complexities of sex, questioning scientific objectivity, and engaging meaningfully with the ethical dilemmas of regulation. I enter this space as an Olympian in the very event that has been at the center of public debate: the women’s 800m in track-and-field, in which I competed against South African champion Caster Semenya. I am also a feminist sociologist who now occupies a unique space in discussions of inclusion in women’s sport. In my paper, I discuss the various dilemmas that I have encountered on this journey: how to gain a seat at the table if sports governing bodies consider my political views to run counter to their own? How to engage my female athlete peers in meaningful, open discussion if they feel threatened by the insights of feminist science studies? How to invite critical reflection on the complex role of race and nation within the regulation of female athlete eligibility? How to avoid silencing women athletes when encouraging their participation in dialogue might invite the expression of anti-trans sentiment? And at what cost to my own wellbeing and career? I discuss how to cope as a feminist social scientist in a polarized public debate, including the invaluable lessons I have learned from mentors and peers.

Developing Ethical Robotics? Interfering as an STS Scholar in an Embedded Ethics Project *Maximilian Braun, Technische Universität München; Ruth Müller, MCTS TU München*

The recent years have seen widespread efforts to govern the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and robotic systems in ways that preserve their widely envisioned benefits while mitigating their potential risks. Ethicists and scholars from the social sciences have been frequently called upon as the relevant experts to find answers to this challenge, which resulted in numerous publications on ethical principles and practices. One approach among these works is ‘embedded ethics’, which suggests to facilitate ethical governance by embedding ethicists and STS scholars early on in technology development projects (McLennan et al. 2020). The embedded scholars ought to actively address ethical and social aspects in the development process and thereby actively contribute to its future trajectory. In our contribution to this panel, we want to reflect on our experiences as embedded social scientist in the Responsible Robotics (RRAI) project. In this project, we collaborate with developers who create robotic applications for elderly care. We want to discuss the epistemic challenges and opportunities that come with our engagement, arguing that it offers important opportunities to balance the currently prevailing emphasis on ‘ethics’ in technology development with important insights from STS. This includes an analytic shift from the implementation of ethical principles towards attending to the ‘tacit’ modes of governance and interference effects from within a project’s organizational boundaries. These are, for example, the impacts of the self-understanding of professional roles of developers, the normative frameworks of academic career systems and the performative effects of the embedded ethics methodology.

Enacting Contemplative Realities: A Case Study of the Healthy Minds Program App *Ana Cristina Lopes*

This presentation will address processes involved in the translation (e.g. Callon 1986; Latour 2005) of certain originally Buddhist ideas and contemplative practices into Western technoscience idioms and their concomitant assimilation into different domains of contemporary societies. It will do so by discussing the Healthy Minds Program (HMP) and related app, which was recently released (July 2020) by the Center for Healthy Minds at University of Wisconsin-Madison. The HMP is described as an “innovative program” that “uses neuroscience, contemplative traditions, and skill-based learning methods to

help you develop the skills for a healthy mind” (<https://hminnovations.org/>). The innovation promised by the program derives in part from recent research developed by the Center and other research institutes that focus on compassion-based meditation and the possibilities for trainable prosocial qualities such as appreciation, kindness and compassion. Besides promoting this extended view of what constitutes contemplative practices, the program also has the ambition of establishing itself as a core framework for research in the field. Indeed, the HMP app is being employed by other research institutes to facilitate their own scientific studies. How is this shift in view being consolidated in practice? How does a program become a core framework for other research? In order to answer these questions among others, this presentation will follow in the footsteps of John Law and others (e.g. Law 2009; Law and Urry 2004) by exploring a performative understanding of these scientific studies in their enactment of new realities connected to the assimilation of contemplative practices into contemporary societies.

Session Organizer:

Jitse Schuurmans, Erasmus University Rotterdam

Chair:

Dara Ivanova, Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management

Discussants:

Iris Wallenburg, institute for Health Policy and Management

Roland Bal, Erasmus University Rotterdam

277. Race and “deadly life-making” in contemporary biomedicine

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

This panel brings together papers that explore biomedical ideas of race that are mobilized beyond the lab under a politics of affirmation (e.g., to target racial health disparities, to include diversity, to secure life, etc). These practices promote particular kinds of relations that aim to foster life but may in fact be deadly, an interrelation that is captured by Ehlers and Krupar’s (2019) notion of “deadly life-making”. By looking at biomedical approaches to health and the governance of life through this analytic, the papers in this panel recognize that death is always inextricable from processes of life-making. Presenters will examine one or more of these forms of life-death relations: life-making practices that obscure death, those that create deathly conditions, and efforts to make live that actually produce death or death effects. Together, the contributions to this panel partake in the analysis of how biomedical ideas of race are strategically mobilized to stake claims and resist race-based injustice or inequality, but they critically expand this analysis by unveiling the deadly effects of these deployments. They also shed light on the methods and practices that maintain oppressions (deadly forms of life) within technoscience.

Participants:

Politics of affirmation and the constant quest for equity for Sickle Cell Disease **Melissa Creary**, *University of Michigan, School of Public Health*

A politics of affirmation is neither neutral, liberatory, or good as explicated by Ehlers and Krupar’s (2019) concept of deadly life-making. It suggests that while the lives of some are deemed valuable enough to affirm, there are others who are abandoned and excluded. Deadly life-making is conceptually linked with bounded justice (Creary, 2021) which argues that when policies and programs are justice-oriented and life-making, they are still bounded by greater socio-historical constraints—often deadly. This paper serves to explore the ways some lives are enhanced via research funding and governmental initiatives while simultaneously obscuring inequities for others. In the medical literature, sickle cell disease (SCD) and cystic fibrosis (CF) are often compared for both their similarity in genetic inheritance as well as difference in prevalence demographics. In two 1970 JAMA and NEJM editorials, a substantial difference in the

research effort for SCD compared with CF was highlighted. In the 2020 Strategic Plan and Blueprint for Action, a National Academies of Sciences proposal to address SCD, CF was recognized again for being rare and having well-organized and well-funded healthcare delivery systems despite having less prevalence. Bounded justice provides the tension between the blueprint’s acknowledgement of racism’s impact on the advancement of SCD and simultaneous recommendation of the Cystic Fibrosis Foundation to serve as a model for the community—without acknowledging the associated privileges of whiteness. The deadly life-making processes embedded in the scientific apparatus for SCD maintain the status quo in the constant quest for equity.

Policing the Pandemic: Racial Profiling in Covid Times **Nadine Ehlers**, *University of Sydney*

Public health surveillance establishes a relation that aims to foster life. Such surveillance functions as an affirmation to track and mitigate biological threats: to make people and whole communities live; to maintain life through safeguarding against these threats. In our contemporary moment, attempts to slow the spread of the Covid-19 virus have seen public health efforts and policing come together in novel ways, to produce what we might think of as ‘pandemic policing.’ This paper takes as a given the long-entrenched intersection of policing and public health in racialized communities but examines how this intersection operates in relation to Covid. It traces various ways the category of race is mobilized beyond the lab and biomedical health terrain in pandemic policing, via practices/technologies/techniques such as digital tracking technologies, waste-water surveillance, infection and mortality data, and enforced quarantine and detention. Looking across various empirical locales—the US, Australia, the UK, and beyond—the paper shows that this surveillance employs predictable forms of racial profiling, always-already positioning black bodies, in particular, as wayward. Rather than safeguarding lives against the virus, and engendering a positive relation of making-live, pandemic policing instead further contains, punishes, and exposes to death racialized populations. It further exposes another relation: the interrelation between the ostensibly life-making modes of surveillance and death-effects.

“Unemployed and With Low Education,” Or Epidemic Containment as Deadly Life-making in Mexico **Vivette Garcia Deister**, *UNAM*

The presidency of Felipe Calderón, which between 2006 and 2012 produced 87K homicides linked to his “narco war”, has been described as the beginning of a violence epidemic, one that has not ceased and continues to take thousands of casualties. In 2016, Mexico’s Secretary of Health declared an epidemiological emergency due to the high incidence of diabetes and obesity in the country. On February 27, 2020, the first case of Covid-19 was detected in Mexico. As cases grew exponentially, Mexico joined the rest of the world in a global sanitary emergency. To date, Mexico has over 2 million confirmed cases of Covid-19 and 186K deaths, a high percentage of which have presented obesity and diabetes as comorbidities. Even as these seem to be isolated phenomena that have their own causes, tempos and dynamics, all three proclaimed epidemics share a striking commonality: they target the same racialized demographic, people who are unemployed and with low education. In this paper I examine the tactics of epidemic containment across these three overlapping scenarios. The analytic of “deadly life-making” (Ehlers and Krupar 2019) helps me to understand how, through explicit affirmations to secure life, the strategies deployed to contain these three epidemics obscure forms of highly selective deaths or uphold the continuation of racialized precarity.

Healthfields: Community-Driven Health Justice or Toxic Blight Renewal? **Shiloh Krupar**, *Georgetown University*

This paper repositions biomedical approaches to health within

the racialized land practices of biomedicine as a development project. US land reuse policies known as “healthfields” seek to enhance public health and ameliorate medical scarcity in underserved BIPOC communities. The strategy relies on prior models of brownfield property redevelopment that convert contaminated, abandoned, or underutilized land to new uses, tied to the private sector and property market understandings of “productivity.” Healthfield projects tether the reuse of brownfield sites to health purposes, namely, local access to healthcare centers and community clinics. Using the framework of “deadly lifemaking” (Ehlers & Krupar 2019), this paper will explore how healthfields can perpetuate ill health and harm. Healthfields reframe land revitalization as an ongoing public health project involving community stewardship of bodies of land and human health. However, the policy framework relies on the racialized logics of property “improvement” and “blight” that target contaminated land in minority communities, potentially leading to displacement and gentrification. Contradictorily, the initiative offers tax breaks and lowers cleanup standards and liability to health projects that remedy toxic blight: Medical facility projects may follow less stringent environmental cleanup standards, thus ensuring that potentially significant (but uncertain) contamination remaining in the land may continue to endanger health. Even as healthfield programs create an opportunity to provide badly needed health services and community-oriented land remedies, they also spur the growth of extractive biomedical development projects that exploit devalued land and further entrench health disparities.

“All we have to do is take the vaccine”: Racializing Vaccine Hesitancy, Obscuring Ongoing Inequalities *Anne Pollock, King's College London*

In national and international media, the COVID vaccine rollout in the United Kingdom has been broadly hailed as swift and successful. After a shambolic governmental response to the pandemic itself that had contributed to one of the highest per capita death tolls in the world, this was welcome news for many. However, there has been a significant thread of media concern about the potential of vaccine hesitancy to impede the vaccine rollout, specifically among Black and minority ethnic communities. This paper is grounded in a close reading of a widely-viewed video campaign created by a group of Black and Asian British celebrities that has urged these communities to get the vaccine. The video debunks a few potential objections – for example that it might contain pork, or a microchip; that it might decrease fertility, or pose long-term health risks – and articulates vaccination as the singular path to back to community and to normal life. Drawing on the lens of “deadly life-making” (Ehlers and Krupar 2019), I argue that this racially and ethnically targeted campaign to promote vaccines obscures the fundamentally unequal enhancement of life/letting die under neoliberal biopolitics, which has structured the unequal burdens of the pandemic just as it has structured health and disease burdens more broadly.

Session Organizer:
Vivette Garcia Deister, UNAM

Chair:
Vivette Garcia Deister, UNAM

278. Situating, transforming, and (de)centering Images of the Futures - I

8:00 to 9:30 am
4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Our current realities are a mess to embrace: the current global pandemic and its disruptions in labor, education, and other socio-technical systems; the increasing political and ontological polarizations and the urgent action against a human-catalyzed climate emergence are challenged our notion of safety, certainty, and even the survival of life on earth (as the ongoing massive extinction, and other fateful events). Our cartesian imaginations in

fiction, planning, modeling, anticipation, and foresight are being defied for the unknown, opening a public demand for new ecological, material, and inter-mutual relations around the globe. A source of these imaginations are images of the future. In 1961, Frederick Polak defined it as “images of the totally other, and they are revolutionary and radical in nature, or they are nothing at all”. Future studies have contributed to popularize these images, (Inayatullah, 2008; Zheltikova & Khokhlova, 2019), which are connected to the movements of decolonial anthropologies and designs (Tlostanova, 2017; Escobar, 2018; Schultz, 2018), as well offer powerful insight for the study of emergent socio-technical imaginaries (Jasanoff, 2015; Konrad & Böhle, 2019). This panel wants to set a conversation around the role of images of the future in STS, in particular projects and practices looking at local, topical, or systemic images. We hope to have contributions to understanding how to situate, expand, nuance, and (de)centered “images of the futures”, to produce alternative realities (like Afro-futurism or Solar-Punk), and to restore more-than-human balances from the unequal, unbalanced, and unfair relations across scales.

Participants:

Refracting Visions: Methodological Oscillations of Images of Future(s) & Images of Technology(ies) *Martin Andrés Perez Comisso, SFIS - Arizona State University*

Images of the future are a theoretical and methodological strategy used in future studies to articulate discourses, narratives, and artifacts that will come—a unit of analysis that allows the practitioners to engage with the uncertain. Visions aren't just pictorial but also discursive and metaphorical representations of the realities from tomorrow. These images are epistemic and situated artifacts also present in technology conversations: the image of development, the discourses of modernity, and the images of emerging tech (like nanotech, artificial intelligence, quantum computing, among others). Despite authors commonly refer to these images, little is theorized in STS and another field about images and visions of technology as an analytical tool for research and public analysis. Haraway (1988) said, "Vision can be good for avoiding binary oppositions." With that premise, and based on a meta-modernist approach developed by the author, I explore the conceptual history of the notions of the "visions of the future" and "visions of technology" based on specialized literature in tech history, future studies, design, and STS. Using as an example a collection of Latin American visions of the future, the results characterize each concept and inform on synergic, contrasting, and potential relations between visions of technology and visions of the future. I aim to extend the methodological potential of visions from future to technology studies, in particular, to observe situated images of technology/future.

Climate Change Unimaginaries: The Depoliticising Gaze of Google's Computer Vision (and What To Do About It) *Warren Pearce, iHuman/Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield*

Climate change imaginaries provide cultural resources that can potentially support political engagement and just responses to the ongoing crisis. STS scholars have highlighted how climate imaginaries that bridge scales of knowledge and meaning have remained elusive (Jasanoff, 2010), the long history of attempts by scientists, activists and media to represent climate change visually (e.g. Mahony & Hulme, 2012), and the increasing importance of digital imagery in political engagement (Ezrahi, 2004). Building on this scholarship, this paper analyses the impact of artificial intelligence, specifically computer vision, on climate change imaginaries. Computer vision is an increasingly pervasive technology that seeks to identify the elements of any given image, which can in turn be used to categorise that image. I argue that, rather than opening up new visions of climate futures, the affordances of computer vision are helping to cement an ‘unimaginary’ of climate change as technical, depoliticised and dehumanised. I illustrate this argument in three parts by focusing on the web's most important visual gatekeeper: Google Images.

First, I review how Google has moved from a page ranking methodology focused on 'authority' to one that foregrounds 'visual consistency'. Second, I provide evidence of this change by using computer vision itself to illustrate image classification processes and effects, showing how the climate unimaginary is stabilising around dehumanised landscapes and scientific charts. Third, I reflect on the impact of these AI-powered dynamics on political engagement, and whether computer vision can be put to more fruitful use in re-imagining climate futures.

Futures to embrace the sun *Neko Pushiana, Wayuu Community; Francisco Zambrano Caviades; Luz Ángela Brito, Independiente; Juan David Reina Roza*

The electrification of the world is a product of the revolutions in thought, behavior, science, and technology, in which different actors of society are immersed. In the Colombian case, the inappropriate use of the territories has generated a displacement of indigenous, Afro-Colombian, and peasant communities in order to exploit the components of each ecosystem in an inordinate manner, especially now called "renewable resources". In La Guajira, land of the Wayuu communities, it has been decided to implement a series of wind projects to complement the national energy supply, invading sacred territories, and without benefiting these communities. Like this intervention, there are hundreds of socio-ecological and even ontological conflicts worldwide. This is why the case study "Technologies to embrace the sun" is a proposal for reinvention and revolution from the knowledge, thoughts, and feelings of the human being where each person has a place. Thus, we can imagine possible futures from the generation of a link between science, ancestral and modern technologies, and knowledge about the generation and use of energy. The design and prototyping of low-cost devices -Ka'i (Sun in Wayunaiki) charger and lamp-, at a practical level, allow to approach the idealization of the world proposed from Solarpunk, towards a broad dialogue that allows to absorb and socialize knowledge among scientists, researchers, engineers, artists and indigenous communities in the territory. It is necessary to create, then, other imaginaries and images of the future beyond the green capitalism imposed from outside and re-create it from the knowing and doing.

Sinofuturist Aesthetics: Technologies of Visual Culture and Future Imaginaries *Virginia L. Conn, Rutgers University*

While sinofuturism as a theoretical concept has emerged only relatively recently, Chinese authors and policymakers have long envisioned the future as an opportunity for a national developmental path that offered an alternative to hegemonic Western visions of progress. Representations of various sinofutures developed out of the same Orientalizing impulses that previously relegated China to a space of backwardsness and barbarism (Niu, Huang, Roh 2015) and which now attribute to it a projected futurity, yet the concept of an alternative national sinofuture is one that Chinese authors and artists have appropriated and weaponized for their own creative ends, without necessarily sharing unified goals. Specifically, with its origins in digital media and visual culture (Lek), sinofuturism is already an image-oriented approach to visualizing the future through an extrapolation of images of the present. In this, it is the natural descendent of mid-century visual materials such as *lian huan hua* (连环画, or "linked picture images"), which depicted deterministic visions of a future postscarcity utopia as a *fait accompli*. By situating the question of "the future" within the dual tracks of visual culture and sinofuturist imaginaries, this presentation argues that the legacy of future studies in China has largely been subject to political evaluation when it is more legible through a techno-aesthetic determinism. How have visual technics—drawn, photographed, painted, or recorded—been utilized not only to imagine a Chinese future (or futures), but also interpellate viewers into bringing such a future about?

Situating sinofuturism: Techno-orientalist fantasies, digital arms

races, and chronopolitical othering *Gabriele de Seta, University of Bergen*

If it were possible to rank the countries that have been most often associated with "the future" over the past two decades, China would most definitely top the charts. After its WTO accession in 2001, and on the heels of its modernization efforts, China has been increasingly represented internationally as a rising economic power proving to be the future of, at first, foreign investment and trade, and successively, of technological development and scientific innovation. Nowhere is this future-oriented narrative more evident than in the domain of digital technologies, and China is widely seen as having successfully leaptfrogged towards a leading position in the information economy, both in terms of scale and growth. In the mid-1990s, cultural theorists started sketching the contours of these future-oriented imaginations of China, identifying them as an emerging "sinofuturist" paradigm that is today current across disciplines and fields. Drawing on ongoing research into sinofuturist representations, this presentation connects them to historical precedents of techno-orientalist imaginaries, frames them in the context of other articulation of futurity in China, and identifies the implications of future-oriented othering for the geopolitics of digital technology. The "chronopolitical othering" implicit in sinofuturism is pivotal in shaping how Chinese science and technology are represented as both threat and opportunity, and how Chinese sociotechnical actors are framed as both unfair competitors and extensions of nation-state agency.

Session Organizer:

Martin Andrés Perez Comisso, SFIS - Arizona State University

279. STS Alter-ed: The Production of Otherness in Technoscientific Enactments

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Michelle Murphy in her keynote address at the 2016 4S/EASTS meeting, "What a Body can't do?" called for STS to attend to alterlife—"a politics of entanglement, kinship, and responsibility" that explicates the material enmeshment of the human body with chemical exposures and environmental violence (7). She claims that bodies are already "more-than-bodies" and "they stretch outward to water, air, ancestors and other beings, that stretches backward to messy histories and forward to something else" (11). Today, we find ourselves in tense entanglements of exclusionist relationalities that reify the boundaries which frame the modern subject and their embodiment. Power structures including religion, racism, law, science, technology contribute to the production of otherness within a technoscientific apparatus like nuclear energy, AI, Big Data etc. (Ali). While STS has extensively focused on inclusion and exclusion of beings in technoscientific enactments, the philosophical, sociological, historical and anthropological treatment of the meanings of "alterity" or otherness that emerge under technoscientific duress remain unaddressed. Calling for an STS of alterity, this panel asks, 1) how and what constitutions of otherness, say human/non-human, is produced in technoscientific enactments? 2) how the boundaries and relations between self and other are made, unmade and reified through technoscientific enactments? 3) are these (alter-ed) relations racial, colonial, imperial, postcolonial, gendered? This panel aims to bring together a large array of research on technoscientific practices and how they produce "otherness." Papers that explicate the production of otherness in the context of environmental justice and contamination, especially radiation contamination, are particularly welcome. Papers may also interpret STS theories including Actor Network Theory (as called for the by Law), New Materialisms, (Crip) Feminist and anti-racist Technoscience using the frames of "othering" and "alterity." Bibliography Ali, Misria S. 2020. "Memorializing Decommissioning: A Nuclear Culture Approach to Safety Culture." *RSA Journal* 31 (2020): 33-58. Law, John. 2002. "Objects and Spaces." *Theory, Culture & Society* 19 (5-6): 91-105. doi:10.1177/026327602761899165. Murphy, Michelle. 2017 "What Can't a Body Do," *Catalyst* 3 (1): 1-15.

https://catalystjournal.org/index.php/catalyst/article/view/28791/pdf_5

Participants:

Aging with drug use: Theorizing with intersectionality, material gerontology and critical drug studies *Aysel Sultan, Frankfurt University of Applied Sciences*

Cultural and critical gerontological literature has long shown that older age has been a factor in healthcare and social exclusion. Drug use and drug treatment are no exceptions, although social studies of drug use in old age are still marginal. At the same time, the marginalization of aging drug users also offers a view of the poorly institutionalized discourse of drug treatment. This discourse has begun to shift with the spread of harm reduction and more patients enrolling into long-term social and medical services such as methadone maintenance treatment. Intersectionality of old age and illicit drug use presents an array of conceptual and methodological challenges to social and critical studies of drug use. Rethinking old age and what aging means within the context and materiality of drug use is possible through the conceptualization of the aging body, materiality, and care. In this sense, this paper's presentation deals with the question of how drug use matters in old age? Thinking in materialist-ontological terms leads to further questions such as how age can be reproduced with(in) drug use, and how illicit drugs (and related paraphernalia) can change and enact the idea of old age? Material conceptualization of age informed by intersectionality is also important because of how old age shapes care and inequalities in healthcare. A particular interest of this paper lies in understanding intersectionality in aging through the contributions of STS, as I argue the two theoretical approaches complement each other well.

Affective Entanglements: Iranian and Iranian-American Gamers on Social Media and World of Warcraft *Melinda Cohoon, University of Washington*

Social media and video games are increasingly a part of everyday life, impacting our social norms and values across the world. Yet, the social phenomenon of connecting on mediated platforms, as it spans across borders, nationality, age groups, and gender, reinvigorates national ties and solidifies political cleavages (Akhavan 2013). My ethnographic and computational social science research elucidates how Iranians in Tehran, Iran, and Iranians across the globe connect and disconnect with one another through the World of Warcraft (WoW), a massive multiplayer online game, and use Twitch.TV, Twitter, and Reddit as a mode of communication post-play. While my research uncovers the interaction between Iranian and Iranian-American women, and the alt-right group in the US during the 2020 presidential election, I also aim to show how Iranians face international constraints, oppression, and lack access to spaces of social media and gaming. I uncover the everyday ordinary affects through the subtleties of online Iranian gamer experiences. I seek to conceptualize how the embodied subject negotiates their social and material subjectivity within online worlds (Dale 2005). Specifically, I parse out subjectivity by exploring the unexplored tensions and intensities of Iranian gamer culture within contexts of toxic masculinity, gender, and labor through participant-observation and data visualizations (Ahmed 2004, 2010). In this vein, the virtual is rendered flesh through attending to the broader rhythms or patterns of an intertwined transnational society by showing online games as (im)material affective entanglements (Vannini and Taggart 2015, 156, Pederson 2013; 737).

Creating Self. Labelling in the Otherkin community *Joanna Ziemna, Adam Mickiewicz University*

The Otherkin are an Internet-based subculture of individuals who identify as other-than-human. The identities created by members of the community can stretch from earthly animals to mythological or otherworldly creatures, such as elves, dragons, aliens, or angels. The community constructs varying labels as means of categorising their unusual experiences. The presented project seeks to explore the Otherkin phenomenon and the ways its representatives construct those labels. Since people who

identify as Otherkin tend to already be a member of various minorities in terms of sexuality, gender, or neurodivergence, instead of letting society define them, they create more and more uncommon identities that are helpful in navigating society that has rejected them. By using MAXQDA and quantitative and qualitative secondary data analysis the project examines the correlation between identifying as Otherkin and being a member of a minority. The project might shed some light on the need to seek and use labels, and on the ways in which underprivileged individuals, as a result of ostracisation, tend to gather in Internet-based communities and may be more prone to autoreflexion, which might prompt them to embrace other nonnormative identities.

To be or not to be? Conference Participation Post- Acceptance; Reflexive Narratives from Kashmir *S. AROKIA MARY, CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF KASHMIR; Mir Insha Farooq, CENTRAL UNIVERSITY OF KASHMIR*

Conferencing is crucial for growth and nexus in academia. Participation in conferences is influenced by numerous factors, ranging from logistics, resources, support systems, social inequalities, freedom from care work and, in some cases, political factors (Henderson and Moreau, 2020; Sabharwal, Henderson & Joseph, 2020). 'To be or not to be?' elaborates on some key issues, primarily political, time zones, graveyard slot and gendered factors that influence the decision to participate or not to participate in a conference post-acceptance in the context of Kashmir. Pandemic induced lockdown on its flip side enabled conferencing virtually. However, the same could not be assumed to be valid for Kashmir, owing to the political decision of restricted slow speed internet (2G; from Jan 2020 to 05th Feb 2021). Using reflexive accounts of the contributors, 'To be or not to be?' analyses and critically reflects on various factors that influence participation post-selection. Primarily, it records the conferencing narratives of two early career female academics from Kashmir. Further, findings elaborate on various individual(gendered), institutional and national level aspects that influence the decision of successfully participating or taking a stand to negotiate with the stakeholders and eventually not participating and recording dissent against the exclusionary nature of a particular conference. In sum, the paper objectively attempts to scrutinize the process, which leads to participation or withdrawal from a conference.

Session Organizer:

Dibyadyuti Roy, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Jodhpur

Chair:

Misria Shaik Ali, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Discussant:

Rahul Mukherjee, University of Pennsylvania

280. Caste as/of Technoscience - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Despite its continued importance as an analytical category in the social life of south asia, and south asians globally, caste as a lens or a category of analysis has historically remained relatively undertheorized in the social studies of science and technology. If at all, caste has largely figured as an identity category in extant work. Can reframing the study of caste as a study of technoscience improve our engagements with caste as a social category as well as that of the social study of science and technology? What conceptual and methodological toolkit would such a move need? How are caste and technoscience intertwined? Is caste an historically morphing assemblage which shapeshifts as new sociotechnical arrangements become possible/are enabled by it? If so, what new ways of thinking about caste are enabled when we approach 'caste' as technoscience? And vice versa, what new ways of thinking about technoscience are enabled as we think about 'technoscience' as caste? This panel invites papers that work with caste not only in axes of identity vis a vis technoscientific worlds but also think through caste as technoscience.

These may range from case studies of sociotechnical assemblages that converge around different kinds of “work,” debates around labour and caste relations, discursive efforts towards castelessness in the name of “merit,” to theoretical pieces that reflect on methodological concerns on the matter which address the co-construction and reification of the caste system through technoscientific practices, imagination and rhetoric in different communities of South Asia and its diaspora.

Participants:

Caste as/of Technoscience: A Case of Sanitation and Domestic Labour in Postcolonial Mumbai *Devesh Khatariker, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay*

In the context of scientific culture in the United States, many studies have highlighted the interconnectedness of race and gender with technoscience. These studies by sociologists like Langdon Winner (1980) and a recent one by Ruha Benjamin (2019) are instrumental in reframing the methods that could be used to study technoscience vis-à-vis race and gender relations. But in South Asia, where the traditional social system continues to prevail in newer forms, the Science and Technology Studies (STS) should be in direct conversation with anthropological studies of caste and gender relations in urban India. This theoretical paper problematizes the absence of large-scale and affordable mechanization in sanitation and domestic work in Indian cities as a failure of modern technoscience. The absence of mechanized methods to clean urban sewers and the predominance of manual scavenging results in the deaths of sanitation workers in India. The paper employs the Actor-Network Theory and anti-Black-box approach that is conscious of power relations within Indian technoscience to investigate following. (a) Why very little businesses have shown interest in producing mechanized instruments for sanitation and domestic work in Mumbai? (b) Why there are only a handful of civil society organizations which work on this cause of expanding the access to mechanized solutions for those who lack them? (c) Does caste and gender relations in urban India affect the invention (or non-invention) of sustainable solutions for devalued forms of labour? By analysing the evolution of technoscience vis-à-vis the Hindu caste system and patriarchy in urban India, this paper contributes to the STS of postcolonial India.

Caste and the Postgenomic Condition: The Politics of Genetically Mapping Sickle Cell Disease in India *Sanghamitra Das, Arizona State University*

In the past decade, sickle cell disease, a recessively inherited blood disorder, has become the focus of biomedicine and public health policies in India. This rare genetic disorder has a global history of being racialized as a “Black disease” (Fullwiley 2011). In India, this disease has been biomedically shown to be prevalent among Adivasi (indigenous tribes) and Dalit-Bahujan (oppressed caste) communities (Panigrahi, Patra, and Khodiar 2015). While public health policies in India describe sickle cell disease as a “tribal” and “lower caste” disease, such an ontological construction of sickle cell disease is challenged by the families and healthcare providers of sickle cell sufferers who do not belong to these communities. Drawing upon ethnographic vignettes and policy analysis, in this paper, I explore how the question of caste is indispensable for theorizing about the post-genomic condition in post-colonial India. Recent scholarship on the social studies of science in India have shown how, like race, genetic blood disorders like sickle cell disease and thalassemia have been mapped onto a caste-based hierarchy justifying biomedical interventions like genetic testing and genetic counselling (Egorova 2010; Chattoo 2018). In this paper, I discuss how the biomedical construction of sickle cell disease as a subaltern (read Adivasi and Dalit-Bahujan) disease in India is co-produced (Jasanoff 2004) with the formation of distinct biosocial formations (Rabinow 2010). These emerging sociotechnical assemblages produce a double marginalization of subaltern sickle cell sufferers: first, by constructing sickle cell

disease as a subaltern disorder in the policy discourse, subaltern biologies (Bharadwaj 2013) are categorized as genetically risky populations that pose future population threats (Chattoo 2018: 35); and second, by an erasure of the sufferings of subaltern sickle cell patients rooted in their social situations within the counter-discourse that challenges the subaltern ontology of sickle cell disease. Through this analysis, I argue that an attention to caste-based hierarchy in investigating the politics of the biomedical management of a “tribal” genetic disorder in India enables interrogating the racializations, local and global, embedded in transnationally mobile biomedical assemblages. References: Bharadwaj, Aditya. 2013. “Subaltern Biology? Local Biologies, Indian Odysseys, and the Pursuit of Human Embryonic Stem Cell Therapies.” *Medical Anthropology* 32 (4): 359–73. <https://doi.org/10.1080/01459740.2013.787533>. Chattoo, Sangeeta. 2018. “Inherited Blood Disorders, Genetic Risk and Global Public Health: Framing ‘Birth Defects’ as Preventable in India.” *Anthropology & Medicine* 25 (1): 30–49. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13648470.2017.1381231>. Egorova, Yulia. 2010. “Castes of Genes? Representing Human Genetic Diversity in India.” *Genomics, Society and Policy* 6 (3): 32. <https://doi.org/10.1186/1746-5354-6-3-32>. Fullwiley, Duana. 2011. *The Enculturated Gene*. <https://press.princeton.edu/books/paperback/9780691123172/the-enculturated-gene>. Jasanoff, Sheila. 2004. *States of Knowledge: The Co-Production of Science and the Social Order*. Routledge. Panigrahi, Sumanta, P. K. Patra, and P. K. Khodiar. 2015. “The Screening and Morbidity Pattern of Sickle Cell Anemia in Chhattisgarh.” *Indian Journal of Hematology and Blood Transfusion* 31 (1): 104–9. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12288-014-0407-z>. Rabinow, Paul. “Artificiality and enlightenment: from sociobiology to biosociality.” *Politix* 2 (2010): 21–46.

The crematorium as a spatial organizer of caste in colonial India *Sohini Chattopadhyay, Columbia University in the City of New York*

This paper studies how the crematoria apparatus spatialized caste practices in colonial and early independent India. In 1896, Calcutta had its first Cremation Society for its British residents and they established a crematorium in 1905, its incinerator imported from France. It soon fell to disuse as very few people used it. A Cremation Society of Bombay existed since 1882, where big industrialists and cotton merchants were members. Social elites hoped these machines would change how upper caste Hindus cremated their dead in open grounds, or how the Parsi community exposed corpses to vultures. But Bombay could not establish a crematorium due to public outcry. Yet, the crematoria apparatus achieved success elsewhere. They were imported in India to replace stigmatized caste burials, and to dispose of unclaimed corpses and dissected parts, leading to Bombay’s first electric crematorium for unclaimed bodies in 1953. Calcutta installed gas crematoria for pauper deaths in a waste disposal ground in 1923, demonstrating a longer history of experimenting with death rites. This paper traces the history of fascination with these big machines that crumbled the body into carbons and negligible remains, and studies the failure to implement it among social elites and the success in using them for bodies of the stigmatized underbelly of urban society. While historians have studied reorganization of death as a part of public health concern, this paper looks at how the crematoria apparatus was used to reorganize and caste practices of death in the colonial cities. Through documents housed in Maharashtra State Archive, Calcutta Municipality Archive and newspapers, this paper demonstrates that the crematoria apparatus was used to spatialize caste and build new hierarchies of death practices. This study will contribute towards understanding how technologies intersect caste and in turn build new spaces of caste practices in cities.

Session Organizer:

Palashi Vaghela, Cornell University

Discussant:

Shivani Kapoor, O P Jindal Global University

281. Celebrating and Critiquing Feminist Inclusion Strategies in Technoscience Communities - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Science and technology communities come in many forms, from the elite community of research scientists within the academy to the myriad grassroots communities that spring up to take direct action on technology policy issues. Yet despite this wide variation in technoscience communities, many continue to reproduce gendered patterns of exclusion visible in science and technology more broadly. This panel provides space for critiquing community practices and structures of exclusion that contribute to limiting who can participate in the production of technoscientific knowledge, who can contribute to decision-making around policy and innovation priorities, and who gets to design the technological products and infrastructure that shape our lives. But, in line with this year's theme of "good relations", it also aims to celebrate successful inclusion strategies, to identify replicable practices for enhancing community diversity, and to highlight radical experiments in relationship-building and community development. We believe that this year, of all years, this celebration of progress is particularly important. We welcome contributions—from any geographical location in the Global South or North—that explore feminist community inclusion strategies from a wide range of theoretical approaches. These could include (but are not limited to): communities of practice; space and place-making; social field theory; identity theory; affect theory; participatory design and co-design practices; and critical making. We also welcome practice-oriented presentations that are not necessarily based in theory. We particularly welcome intersectional contributions that look at issues of gender inclusion/exclusion alongside axes of "race", ethnicity, class, (dis)ability, transgender status, sexual identity, etc.

Participants:

Caring For Diversity In IT – Transfeminist Community Building Practices In Argentina *Solange Martinez Demarco*, Ruhr University Bochum

Research on gender and ICT has been profuse and acknowledges the particular difficulty that women and LGBTQ+ people face when trying to participate in the IT field. In order to increase diversity many women and allies' groups flourished at the beginning of the XXI century, demanding diversity in technology for reasons such as joy, agency, empowerment, and equality with agendas that are distinctive from those of higher education, governments, or companies due to their voluntaristic character (Dunbar-Hester 2019). Although there is scholarship inquiring into their values, ideals, motivations, and practices of care (Dunbar-Hester, 2020), these analyses are based on groups located in the Global North, mainly in the USA and Canada. In this presentation the focus will be on a transfeminist IT community of Argentina that I have been studying for some months and of which I am part of. The interviews I have conducted with some of the members and the observations I have gathered support the need for research into the specificities of such groups in the Global South. Values, motivations, practices and technologies must always be re-negotiated for the community to move forward. Participation is restricted: cis men are excluded. Open technologies are promoted, but neo-colonial, neoliberal, and extractivist technological infrastructures are not rejected. In this sense, they draw boundaries, they identify certain problems as matters of care deserving of its attachment and commitment and dismissing others (Martin et al., 2015).

Relational Engineering Practices: Insights From a Feminist Data Science Lab *Kelly Wagman*, The University Of Chicago

This paper looks at how feminist principles are operationalized in an engineering space. Many efforts to increase diversity in engineering in the US focus on a neoliberal idea that individual women and underrepresented minorities should improve their

skills and confidence (e.g. improving the "pipeline," Metcalf 2010). Drawing on participant observation at a self-described "feminist" data science lab housed at a large US research university and interviews with women and non-binary engineers, I found a focus on equitable and inclusive cultural values—an emphasis on "good relations" among members. Their practices included micro-affirmations, embracing ambiguity and collective decision making, valuing social intelligence and lived experience, and making time/space for experimental outputs such as zines. I argue that these practices refute the idea of a "quality-diversity" tradeoff (Seron et al 2018) by reframing what makes "good engineering." Additionally, the lab rejected an assumption found in dominant engineering spaces that some labor is "technical"/hard and thus masculinized while other labor is "non-technical"/soft and thus feminized, and the associated "technical peacocking" performed to show off feats of technical mastery (Turtle & Papert 1990; Ensmenger 2015). By shifting what the engineering culture values—away from an emphasis on technical dominance, right answers, and quantitative success metrics—this feminist data science lab has been able to create a space where members with a range of identities trust each other and feel safe and supported to pursue the research that matters to them.

Sulá Batsú: A Feminist Technopolitics of Care *Firuzeh Shokooh-Valle*, Franklin and Marshall College

In the past 20 years, there has been a race to include women and other marginalized communities in the data society. The importance of integrating women as users, producers, consumers, designers and developers of technologies has become a global mantra against inequality. Prominent strategies include capacity building and training in digital information and communication technologies (ICTs), ICTs for entrepreneurship, and fostering the participation and retention of women in science and technology fields in education and the workforce. But this exciting future being constructed, in which women are considered key figures full of potentiality, contains in its fold subtle, and not so subtle, forms of violence and exclusion. At the same time, feminist technology activists practice a politics of care grounded in solidarity that represents an important site of resistance. Drawing from ethnographic research from 2014-2019, I examine the way in which the grassroots technology-focused feminist cooperative Sulá Batsú, in Costa Rica, practices solidarity challenging colonizing and market-centered strategies by forging collectivized ways of living and working. My paper advances Feminist STS scholarship on the politics of care and the complex relationships among people, objects, and place: the ways in which care is both emancipatory and urgent, as well as uncomfortable and entangled in histories of violence.

Session Organizers:

Em O'Sullivan, University College London

Isha Bhallamudi, University of California, Irvine

Patricia Pena, University of Chile, Institute of Image and Communication

282. Confronting Worlds: The Concept of "World" and its Stakes - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

The world is at stake. Pandemics, climate change, species extinctions, and toxic waste confront policy-makers, scientists, artists, activists, and citizens from around the planet. But what does it mean to be in a world? Are there many worlds or just one? And what kinds of worlds do we want to make? If worlds, as Donna Haraway writes, are not given so much as made, then what other worlds are possible? And how can they be brought into being? "Worlds" and "worlding" have emerged as productive theoretical and practical concepts in science studies as well as other fields. "World" is a seductive concept because of its expansiveness, drawing attention to the relationships between the global, the planetary, and the (other)worldly. Following Jakob Von Uexküll, "world" can make inroads into nonhuman or multispecies domains. "Worlding" inspires flights of imagination, as in

the world-building stories of speculative fiction. “World” is helpful in thinking about incommensurabilities and alterities. Scholars have mobilized “world” to think of culture and context differently, as an alternative to fraught analytics such as the “global” or “scalability” and their imperial and universalizing ambitions. In this session, we invite presentations that critically reflect on the ordering concept of “world” and to consider new directions for investigating the world or worlds in science studies. What does this concept afford us? How might worlds serve epistemically, ontologically, or politically? What are the ethical stakes of worlds or worlding? We welcome traditional or multimodal presentations that explore these questions.

Participants:

Worlds Away From Here: Snowball Earth and Icy Speculation

Julianne Yip, Mitacs

World-building is a key tool in speculative fiction. It is the process through which writers craft multidimensional worlds that are believable because they have an internal logic of their own. As STS and multispecies ethnographers have shown, world-building is not just a tool to spin speculative fiction, but a literal process through which nonhumans such as ice, mushrooms, and microbes produce worlds today. This paper explores what it means for sea ice to world and the possibility that nonhumans can speculate worlds otherwise, too (Clark et al. 2018). In particular, I explore the epistemic spaces that scientific knowledge of sea ice opens up. Sea ice profoundly influences the structure of ecosystems in the Arctic and Antarctic regions of today, giving rise to worlds rich in diverse life-forms and relationships. That said, geological evidence and computer models demonstrate that sea ice has also helped usher in global freeze-overs in Earth’s history that extinguished previous life-forms. Sea ice, in short, is both a world-making and world-destroying entity. What kind of worlding is this, which leads just as equally to an unbecoming as much as a coming-into-being, or “becomings-with”? Sea ice suggests a kind of worlding that does not take life (or death) as its endpoint. Can this be considered “worlding”? I close by considering how speculative fiction as an experimental mode of theorizing (Wolf-Meyer 2019) can help convey the implications of sea ice on world-building and nonhuman forms of speculation.

Scalar Worlds in Environmental Science and Governance:

Watershed to Cryosphere Jeremy Trombley

Scalar concepts are world-building projects that often emerge out of scientific knowledge production. Enacted through the construction of data infrastructures and speculative practices like computational modeling, scalar projects articulate worlds that cut across the traditional structures of the nation-state. But what kinds of world are these concepts and practices producing? And what happens when they become entangled with traditional forms of governance? In this presentation, I juxtapose two scalar projects - the watershed and the cryosphere - to see what kinds of agencies, interests, and meanings are produced through their world-building. For the watershed, we turn to the Chesapeake Bay and its drainage basin. The 40-plus year project of defining, conceptualizing, and governing the watershed for the Chesapeake Bay has shifted organizational and institutional relationships within the region. In this context, the watershed localizes responsibility, and draws attention downward in ways that border on surveillance and over-emphasize individual agency as market participation. For the cryosphere, we look to the Pacific Northwest and the relatively small and unappreciated glaciers that crown its volcanic peaks. As a global concept, the cryosphere links these glaciers to fragmented landscapes of ice in the polar regions, mountainous landscapes, and oceans around the world. In that sense, it globalizes responsibility, and draws attention upward in ways that can often constrain agency to adaptive response. These worlds remain familiar - bounded within the articulations of neoliberal capitalism. I ask how scalar concepts might be deployed otherwise, alongside other world-building projects, and what other worlds might be created with

them?

Cultivated and Crowdsourced Worlds: Citizen science, sourdough companions, and microbial perspectives *Darcie A DeAngelo, University of Oklahoma*

Yeast tells us that the average indoor North American atmosphere is the same as the outdoor climate of western Kenya. This is one of the takeaway findings from a crowdsourced science experiment run by microbiologists and ecologists at North Carolina State’s Rob Dunn lab. The lab collects and analyzes sourdough starters from participants in a global study under “Your Wild Life Projects.” For the yeast, these African and American atmospheres are the same. Implicit in that connection is the lab’s configuration of global geography and human-nonhuman connections. People share microbial encounters and could, according to the lab, share the perspectives of the microbes themselves. The “Sourdough Project” uses methods to not only think with yeast, but also think like yeast. The lab asks people to send them samples of their sourdough starter and to answer a questionnaire to describe it. The spring of 2020 represents an apex in this research project as the lab recruited even more “citizen scientists” during the pandemic, when most who can physically isolate and stay home. Privileged and unprivileged participants alike, though, cultivate newfound companions, sourdough starters, at the behest of the lab and other impetuses to counter loneliness and bread shortages. The companionship of humans and microbial communities were characterized through a series of sensorial encounters. Humans describe listening to their starters and, in listening, think like yeast by imagining remapped worlds and reconfigured categories of cultivated and wild. This paper investigates what worlding becomes possible through yeasty cultivations of results and “community.”

Utopian Worlding: A Radical Practice or a Sign of Privilege?

Hannah Cowan, King's College London; Charlotte Kühlbrandt, King's College London

Our project set out to critique our university’s public promise, to ‘make the world a better place’. We found that the ‘better’ is rarely discussed, and scientists partake in implicit worlding practices which may not mean better for everyone. We’re intervening on these implicit processes by constructing deliberate conversations between local young people who will live in these future worlds, and researchers who (arguably) have more power over the worlds that get made. Inspired by young climate activists demanding that they are the future, we decided to work with historically activist thought on utopias and hope. We work with Bloch’s understanding of the responsibility of hope and Levitas’ utopia as method, to be creative in our participatory work with young people. But there are also dangers of worlding with utopias. Firstly, you can constantly push the good to the prospective future and leave the present in shortage of any hope in practice. Secondly, whilst the young people we’re working with are more globally connected than ever, they are situated in very specific worlds, with many intersecting sites of disprivilege. Whilst we have attended to temporalities by calling the project Utopia Now!, and bringing some utopian practices back into the present, we’re still struggling with the responsibilities of not over promising when there is so much push back for change. In this paper we therefore consider how we can work with utopia as a worlding method which accounts for both its radical potential and its propensity to be a privileged practice.

Session Organizers:

Julianne Yip, Mitacs
Darcie A DeAngelo, University of Oklahoma
Fiona Gedeon Achi

Chair:

Jonathan Wald, McGill University

283. Transforming the Development & Governance of

Pharmaceuticals - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Major changes are underway within the pharmaceutical sector that are associated with shifts in research, innovation and business models from blockbuster products intended for large patient populations to more niche products designed for smaller, more targeted populations. Innovation is underway in how drugs are being researched and developed, and how they are being manufactured, used, evaluated, licensed and paid for. While some of these changes are tied to genomics and the rise of personalized medicine, others result of patient activism and disease politics. These technical and political developments put pressure on public regulators and payers, resulting in novel forms of governance, including the use of real world data and conditional reimbursement. This panel builds on STS scholarship on the socio-technical production of pharmaceutical knowledge, as well as its material and biopolitical impacts. We invite papers from a range of international perspectives that critically analyze these transformations, as well as those that highlight forms of alternative pharmaceutical practices and methods that are more sustainable and offer more just and equitable access to treatments. Topics may include but are not limited to: – Forms of open pharmaceutical innovation – Industry dynamics and changing business models – Patient groups and new forms of knowledge production – R&D partnerships across public, not-for-profit and/or private sector – Drug repurposing and off-label use – Changing regulatory knowledge and forms of evaluation – Pharmaceutical pricing and access – Novel access arrangement and alternative regulatory frameworks for coverage – Future health care system sustainability and social solidarity.

Participants:

Price as an epistemic and a political object: An inquiry into “the most expensive drug ever” *Liliana Doganova, Mines ParisTech; Vololona Rabeharisoa, Ecole Nationale Supérieure des Mines de Paris*

Approved by the FDA in May 2019, Zolgensma became famous for being “the most expensive drug ever.” Zolgensma is a gene therapy for infants suffering from spinal muscular atrophy. The price that Novartis obtained for this one-time treatment (\$2.1 millions) provoked astonishment in the rare disease community and beyond. The case of Zolgensma offers a fruitful entry point into the exploration of valuation processes and the formation of prices in the biopharmaceutical industry. We analyse the controversies triggered by the announcement of the price of Zolgensma in order to shed light on the ways in which drug prices are problematized, the rationales brought forward to account for the value of drugs, the narratives and calculations in which they are embedded, and the different actors with whom they are associated. Our analysis shows that, in the controversies over Zolgensma, price is problematized both as an epistemic and a political object. We discuss the competing theories of the value of drugs and the determinants of their prices (namely, “value-based” vs. “cost-based” approaches) that have come to the fore, and the different forms of critique that they afford. We argue that the problematization of price as an epistemic object, which lends itself to processes of knowledge production and becomes entangled with claims over the “truth” of values and costs, is deeply interwoven with the problematization of price as a political object, which opens up debates on the organization of the biopharmaceutical industry and the limits of the economic valuation of health.

Building the future of gene therapy: the challenge of delivering, valuing, and assessing novel biological medicines *Paul Martin, Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield*

After 30 years of clinical development gene therapy is finally reaching the market in a wave of treatments for rare genetic diseases. Many of these are one off ‘cures’ for conditions affecting tiny populations of children and are very expensive. E.g. Zolgensma for the treatment of spinal muscular atrophy cost

>\$1.5M in the USA. In response, healthcare providers are establishing new models of reimbursement based on value based pricing. Rather than an up-front fee there are proposals for something closer to an annual subscription, with ongoing payment conditional on results. However, the evaluation of these therapies faces many challenges, including how long the treatment is effective for, if it needs repeating or modifying, and long-term side-effects. Manufacturers are also developing new business models, including product improvement regimens, and offering lifetime cover of the condition as part of a comprehensive treatment plan. These novel models of payment and life-cycle management will depend on establishing new infrastructures to administer and follow-up patients. The creation of these evaluation processes, reimbursement models and service infrastructures will have a profound effect on the viability and availability of gene therapy and may provide a template for other regenerative medicine. This paper, based on a review of regulatory documents, firm strategies and analysis of online discussions and webinars, will chart the socio-technical imaginaries guiding the commercial development of gene therapy, the co-construction of multiple forms of value and the shaping of services. It will conclude by sketching out different possible trajectories for this emerging field.

Alternative Frameworks for Pharmaceutical Coverage:

Canadian Fabry Disease Initiative *Shir Grunebaum, York University; Conor Douglas, York University*

One of the central regulatory challenges facing drugs for rare diseases are their uncertain evidentiary profiles. Inherently small numbers of patients for a particular rare disease often makes it difficult to produce the kinds of clinical trial data that regulators are accustomed to and comfortable with. In the face of such uncertainty that is characterized by drugs for rare diseases, transformations are taking place in pharmaceutical governance that are allowing patients access to treatments while data surrounding efficacy is subsequently collected so that more informed coverage/payment decisions can be made. This paper reports on one such case of these emerging alternative frameworks for coverage in the Canadian Fabry Disease Initiative (CFDI). This initiative was established after the Canadian Agency for Drugs and Technologies in Health (CADTH) recommended against coverage of the enzyme replacement treatment for Fabry Disease arguing that “the impact of clinically meaningful outcomes has not been proven in randomized trials or observational studies to date”. Here we track the establishment of the CFDI and their work in securing over 360 patients publicly funded access to the treatment while simultaneously collecting real-world data on their outcomes. We argue that this initiative represents a kind of “social pharmaceutical innovation” (or SPIN) in which pharmaceutical governance is harnessing new ways to ensure that patients with rare diseases are granted early access to much needed treatment. We also explore the extent to which this stands to be a pathway that can potentially be replicated for other new treatments.

Personal debt, orphan drugs and healthcare system

sustainability in Chile *Carlos Novas, Carleton University*

Based on the secondary analysis of quantitative and qualitative data collected by the Federación Chilena de Enfermedades Raras (FECHER: Chilean Federation of Rare Diseases) as part of the first national survey of rare diseases in this country, this paper explores the forms of personal debt incurred by many Chilean families as they seek a diagnosis or treatment for their illness. One of the findings of this survey is that many patients and their family’s resort to charitable fundraising or to private lenders to pay for the costs associated with the diagnosis and treatment of their rare disease. These expenses often result in unsustainable debt levels leading some participants in this study to experience significant stress, anxiety, sell personal possessions or declare bankruptcy. This paper seeks to address a gap in the literature on rare diseases and orphan drugs through focussing on the personal

forms of indebtedness associated with the diagnosis and treatment of a rare disease. Chile makes an interesting case study to explore this topic as it has developed legislation in 2015 (Ley Ricarte Soto) to fund orphan drugs for a select number of rare diseases. Secondly, Chile's private and public healthcare system often requires patients to pay out-of-pocket for a number of diagnostic services or medical treatments. As in other national jurisdictions, one of the key debates that has arisen in Chile is the affordability of providing specialist medical services to rare disease patients alongside the high costs of orphan drugs. In a country characterized by significant income and health inequalities, this paper explores the question of affordability in two senses: one, the personal indebtedness that many Chilean rare disease patients and their families experience because of their condition; and secondly, the broader question of the affordability of specialist diagnostic services and high-cost orphan drugs in a country that struggles to meet primary health care needs. Through exploring the relationship between personal debt and healthcare system sustainability this paper aims to explore how debt logics inform the governance of orphan drugs and rare diseases.

Session Organizers:

Conor Douglas, York University

Paul Martin, Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield

Tineke Kleinhout-Vliek, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University

Chair:

Rob Hagendijk, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research, University of Amsterdam

284. Craft, Computers, and Conquest: Renegotiating relations - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Situated Computations is an approach to design and computation that grounds technologies in the social world by acknowledging the historical, cultural, and material contexts of designing and making. It acknowledges and responds to a setting's social and technological infrastructures, and refuses to remain ignorant of economic and political structures that shape it (Noel 2020). In conversation with the conference theme, we invite scholarship that reflects on manual and digital practices to reveal ways in which existing and new oppressions in these sites are maintained or challenged. Our purpose is to examine manual and technological practices inside and outside academia through STS lenses of feminism, post-colonialism, and justice. We ask: How might analog and digital methods contribute to, destroy, or bridge long standing oppressions and strategic sortings of society? How might we conceptualize "good" relations in these practices to frame and enact new relations that confront colonialism, racism, and inequality? We invite works that explore theories, methods and expressions around craft, justice, and technology. How might praxis in situated computations help us identify and reclaim marginalized spaces? What new academic spaces might we reimagine to renegotiate and challenge power relations between those "inside" and those "outside" academia? What links may we draw between the lived experiences of craftspersons and the design of technological systems? Our goal is to imagine how praxis between craft and technological systems can be a source of theoretical and methodological interventions that can attend to racism, inequality and other oppressions in technoscience.

Participants:

Virtually Amish **Lindsay Ems**, *Butler University*

My forthcoming book (MIT Press), *Virtually Amish*, is an ethnographic study of the adoption, design and use of digital communication technologies among members of Old Order Amish communities. Today it is increasingly common for the Amish to adopt computers, the internet and mobile devices in calculated ways to remain competitive in business. Often the use of these devices blends into the personal sphere as well. The book is notable for its empirical observations that show shared

values are key to determining patterns of technology use in Amish communities. In particular, the Amish consider their own cultural, social, political and religious autonomy in deciding how to engage with a broader social and economic system as technologies are essential to the mediation of these relationships. Amish communities are in the process of determining how to navigate the social forces that have come along with, what theorists like Shoshana Zuboff (2019) call, high-tech capitalism. Amish people describe technologies as both functional tools and symbols of engagement with, and resistance to the external social world. In some cases the Amish have configured technologies and designed devices that better align with their values as they are literally and figuratively bridges that connect their separatist communities to an alternative reality. If not properly mitigated, they feel this external world has the potential to erode their culture and religion from the outside in. Decisions about technologies are productive sites of struggle that enable the Amish to create and sustain a dynamic social and cultural sanctuary where their way of life can thrive while resisting the disempowering aspects of the world around them. There are few modern examples of everyday people who have found a sweet spot in which their participation in the economy allows them to acquire resources that can be used to fulfill their social, cultural and political desires regardless of whether or not they align with the system's. Remarkably, members of Amish communities do just this.

Hackerspaces as technofeminist sites for situated, computational practice **Annika Richterich**, *University of Sussex*

Hackerspaces are physical community spaces, where members cultivate computational expertise and craftsmanship. While hackerspaces facilitate digital skills and foster civic innovation, not everyone equally benefits from potential opportunities for learning and creativity. Many hackerspaces struggle with issues related to communal homogeneity, being dominantly frequented by white, male members. Underrepresented groups, e.g. persons self-identifying as female or non-binary, have experienced discrimination and harassment. In response, explicitly feminist hackerspaces – usually women-centred/women-only communities – were founded. Examples are Mz*Baltazar's Laboratory (Vienna), MariaLab (São Paulo), and Double Union (San Francisco). The paper starts from the question how such communities choose, discuss, and situate digital technology. I argue that hackerspaces have the potential to act as technofeminist sites for situated, computational practices. These practices are 'situated' in two respects: first, they reflect more 'generic' aspects of peer-to-peer learning, as outlined in Lave and Wenger's work on "communities of practice"; second, they incorporate technofeminist, intersectional insights, questioning the societal implications of technology. Thereby, they reject and expose a fallacy that Donna Haraway criticised as "the god trick": tech's alleged neutrality, concealing and maintaining the – often white, male, and heterosexually defined – norms implied in computational devices. Methodologically, the paper draws on a case-study approach, presenting qualitative research on feminist hackerspaces in Europe, North and South America. Empirical insight into how women productively engage with technology remains scarce. While there are indeed fewer women working in tech than men, this much-repeated truism has not only fed into gendered misconceptions: it also comes along with a tendency to disregard women's contributions in tech. Feminist STS attempts to tackle this disregard, though remains the exception. The paper aims to highlight, and contribute to, this strand in STS.

Letters To Editors: An Ongoing Correspondence **Katherine Bennett**, *Georgia Institute of Technology*; **Michael Nitsche**, *Georgia Institute of Technology*; **Susana M. Morris**, *Georgia Institute of Technology*

This paper discusses Letters To Editors, a digital craft project that considers historic interactions between race, gender, and place. The project combines text, textile, and computational

media to ask how these media register social and environmental relationships specific to transitioning agricultural production in Jim Crow-era United States. Our reproductions of letters between a Georgia farmer (Bennett 1944) and Pulitzer-winning newspaper editor (McGill 1944) make these relationships explicit in text extracted from their correspondence and an editorial published in the Atlanta Constitution. Careful editing and selective (re)publication of Bennett's raced and gendered letters excavate a message of environmental justice grounded in the labor of reviving farmland degraded by cotton plantations. Inspired by material and craft-based designs (Devendorf/Rosner 2017), Letters To Editors combines analog and digital technologies of weaving, sewing, sensing, and coding toward a material dialogue (Nitsche/Zheng 2018) with cotton and rayon, a forestry product that replaced cotton in Southern textile mills during World War II. Nonhuman editors first revised the hybrid letter-objects, which were buried for three months among the communicative root networks of trees and mushrooms at the Bennett farm. Embedded sensors recorded soil hydration and temperatures altered by climate change and brutal to forest networks. The farm's forester and a local textile artist-farmer next revised the exhumed and marked-up letters, continuing the dialogue with materials and tools of today's practices. Connecting Afrofuturism (Everett 2002) and New Materialism (Barad 2007) to STS (Tsing 2015), the project traces ways that media both perpetuate and change social and environmental relations.

Session Organizer:

Hayri Dortdivanlioglu, Georgia Institute of Technology

Discussant:

Vernelle A Noel, Georgia Institute of Technology

285. Data-Based Biomedicine: Legacies, Frictions, Ontologies I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Biomedicine increasingly relies upon the production, gathering, curation, organization, and sharing of large volumes of data through databases (Chow-White and García-Sancho, 2012). Building upon social studies of computing and biomedicine, this panel investigates data-based biomedicine as it emerges from situated practices of scientific activity. It addresses, but is not limited to, three sets of interrelated questions: First, what are the socio-historical drivers of these 'database-ization' processes? While links between computer and biomedical sciences – particularly in relation to genomics – have been usefully sketched out (Garcia-Sancho, 2011), much remains to be done regarding how biomedical data 'got its bases' (Haigh, 2009). Second, how does data-based biomedicine effectively assemble technological (algorithms, chips, software) and organizational (consortia, standards, benchmarks) configurations, and how is this new 'style of practice' (Keating and Cambrosio, 2012) stabilized in a diversity of domains of biomedicine (e.g. cancer, infectious diseases, public health)? Third, how are data of biological (e.g. 'omics' data), biographical and/or social processes (e.g. social capital, social belongings, patient-reported outcomes, scores of psychosocial complexity) assembled into data-based understandings of health and illness? Making data visible and reliable to as many practitioners as possible entails an increasing work to produce, relate, and standardize biomedical and socio-epidemiological data (Bossen et al., 2019). Through what inclusions/exclusions are bio-social ontologies of health emerging from the intelligibility and interoperability of these data? In parallel to historical focus on path dependencies, the panel invites empirical and conceptual socio-anthropological contributions highlighting the disruptive alignments and frictions (Edwards et al., 2011) that shape data-based biomedicine.

Participants:

Data Ontologies and Organisation in Digital Healthcare - the case of the international standard Health Level 7 *Tsvetelina Hristova, Institute for Culture & Society, Western Sydney University*

What are the ruptures that take place in the processes of translation between digital data ontologies and organisational

processes and structure in healthcare systems? My analysis focuses on the international standard for digital medical data in exchange – Health Level 7. This standard, developed in the 1980s in the US and later adopted worldwide, is concerned with the transferability and interoperability of medical data. Drawing on interviews with members of the organisation in Australia and India, archival document analysis, and analysis of the three versions of this standard, I examine the processes of mapping between the organisation of healthcare systems and the data ontologies and relations codified through the standard. I analyse three versions of the standard, which offer three different visions to the possibility of this mutual mapping through deliberations on the role of communication, linguistic performativity, and the operationalisation of platform logic and interfaces. In each of these versions of Health Level 7, data ontologies and the structure of data relations are contingent on the epistemological dialogues between digital healthcare and digital data standards and infrastructures, on one hand, and the ambition of HL7 to achieve complete mapping of organisational roles, events, and relations through the standard.

Logics Of Data Control And The Emergence Of Deep Learning In Medical Imaging *David Barberá-Tomás, Ingenio (CSIC-UPV) Universitat Politècnica de València*

We propose a framework for understanding the emergence deep learning in the field of medical imaging, where collaborations between radiologists and computer scientists from universities, companies and hospitals for developing quantified parameters from digital medical images for diagnosing several diseases have raised high and, so far, largely unsuccessful expectations in the last decades. The framework synthesises contributions from two research trends concerned with the digital transformations of collaborative knowledge production. First, as recent STS studies on the control of knowledge objects in domains such as genomics have shown (Hilgartner, 2017; see also Hilgartner and Brandt-Rauf, 1994), the analysis of logics of data control is essential for understanding the unfolding of collaborative digital innovation processes. Data control logics refer to the set of values, practices and rules that govern access to data in the field of digital innovation. Second, we borrow from the information systems literature (Faij et al., 2020) the notion of technological affordances, Logics of data control can be "activated" by a new digital technology (such as deep learning) thanks to the "affordances" that emerge from the interaction between humans and technologies (Faik et al., 2021). References: Faik, I., Barrett, M. and Oborn, F. (2020). How information technology matters in soci-etal change: an affordance-based institutional logics perspective. *MIS Quarterly*, 44(3). Hilgartner, S. (2017). *Reordering life: knowledge and control in the genomics revolution*. MIT Press. Hilgartner, S., and Brandt-Rauf, S. I. (1994). Data access, ownership, and control: Toward empirical studies of access practices. *Science Communication*, 15(4), 355-372.

Session Organizers:

Luca Chiapperino, University of Lausanne

Nils Graber, STS Lab, University of Lausanne

Francesco Panese, University of Lausanne, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences

Discussants:

Nolwenn Bühler, STS Lab, University of Lausanne

Florian Jatón, STS Lab, University of Lausanne

286. Diseased Landscapes: Health and Illness in Territories of Extraction - III - VIOLENCE

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Through the theme of Diseased Landscapes, this panel explores how the nexus of extractivism and political conflict affects environmental and human health. It aims at bringing together efforts in scholarly practice—

including art-based methodologies and activist-oriented research—to historically, politically, and socially situate disease, toxins, pathogens, non-humans, and bodily dysfunction in violent geographies produced by legal and illegal extractivism. We ask how the health conditions of the environment and the body become entangled in places dominated by extractivist economies. What difference does it make to tell stories of armed violence, gendered and racialized dispossession, capitalism, mining, and agrarian expansion through human and more-than-human experiences of health and illness? How are evidence and ignorance about bodies and landscapes produced, used, and abused in contexts marked by extractivist activities? And finally, what practices, methods, and interventions are helpful to establish good relations, capable of disrupting the combined production of disease and violence in old, new, and future territories of extraction?

Participants:

Armed conflict and environmental health: impacts on collective health due to environmental violence in Colombia *Fabian Mendez, Universidad del Valle; Irene Vélez-Torres, Universidad del Valle*

Multiple actions affect the well-being of ecosystems and the health of all living beings as consequence of environmental violence in civil wars and armed conflicts. In this scoping review we analyze the health effects of the Colombian armed conflict between 1970-2015 in three categories of environmental violence: pipeline bombing, informal gold mining, and aerial spraying of glyphosate for the eradication of illicit crops. We searched for articles in three databases of indexed journals, in digital repositories of local universities, as well as in websites of newspapers, and official repositories of domestic policy documents in which the armed conflict intertwines with health and the environment. The analysis aims at scrutinize the nexus between the armed conflict, the environment, and the integrated human health impacts. Conceptual diagrams were built to present impacts of environmental violence in five dimensions of ecological and social systems. Actions of environmental violence disproportionately affect regions and ethnic groups in which greater social and economic vulnerability increases susceptibility and enhances disease. In consequence, reparation must consider the vulnerabilities and the historical inequities that communities have experienced, while non-repetition entails the resolution of structural social injustices and damaging consequences of the capitalist exploitation of nature.

Cursed Geographies? Slow violence and the armed conflict in Colombia *Irene Vélez-Torres, Universidad del Valle; Fabian Méndez, Universidad del Valle*

Geographies of extraction have been closely entangled with dispossession and armed conflicts, thus the idea has been coined that the abundance of resources can be a curse for developing countries. On the one hand, it has been widely documented how conflicts over the access of environmental assets turn into armed confrontations. On the other hand, there is growing evidence of the negative impacts that armed conflicts create on socio-ecological relationships. But this two-side story becomes more complex when structural and slow violence are taken into account as root causes of war and relevant process of environment deprivation and degradation. To make sense of this complexity, we inquire the nexus between slow violence, structural violence and armed conflict in three categories of environmental violence in Colombia. We look at the interface between governmental extractivism, oil pipe bombing by left-wing guerrillas, and the degradation of traditional livelihoods of communities living on the extractive oil frontiers. We research on the economic dependency of coca-growing peasants, the War on Drugs led by the state and supported by international governments and agencies, and the socio-ecological effects of eradication programs. Last but not least, we study the community dilemmas and struggles to fight the use of mercury in Artisanal Gold Mining in the context of expanding illegal economies used

and secured by armed groups in contemporary gold bonanzas.

Mining Violence: Producing Life and Risk in Kenya's Artisanal Gold Mines *Jessica Worl, Davidson College*

Kenya is attempting to market itself as the next mining frontier echoing colonial rhetoric from the 1930s designed to attract white settlers to western Kenya's newly discovered gold fields. The Kakamega Gold Rush led to the construction of two, parallel mining sectors: the first, legal, protected, and occupied by white settlers; and the second, illegal, policed, and marked by the participation of black Kenyan miners and Indian traders. Today, legal gold mining has all but disappeared, but its informal gold mining communities remain, attracting the attention of state regulatory bodies, international development organizations and nongovernmental organizations concerned with the use of mercury to process gold. Drawing on Ann Stoler's concept of imperial debris, I trace the emergence of Kenya's illegal gold mining communities to the contemporary moment to examine how current environmental and social violence associated with illegal gold mining communities are an extension of colonial policies. Further, current attempts to monitor mercury pollution and exposure act both to call attention to the environmental health implications of informal gold mining operations while establishing what Huggins et al. term "cartographies of concern," marking particular communities in need of regulation and increased enforcement, further marginalizing some of western Kenya's most vulnerable communities. I argue that paying attention to how miners produce a life on Kenya's gold deposits and respond to and understand risk yields insight into how social and environmental problems produced in these mining sites can be resolved.

When diseases have no name: discourse control and health problems invisibilization in a mining territory. The case of Tierra Amarilla, Atacama Region (Chile). *Claudio Broitman Rojas, Universidad Andrés Bello*

Landscapes and territories can be represented in different ways. This representation is usually dominated, in terms of enunciation, by actors that have the discourse control: the medias, the corporate social responsibility or even the public institution are commonly places where the political and the economic power express its own representations. There is a small town in the Atacama Region (Chile), Tierra Amarilla, where inhabitants have little possibilities of representation. Living for decades in precarious conditions, they were told that the installation of medium and big mining activities would change their own quality of life. But there is just a few among them that works on mining. Instead, they have to live in worst conditions compared before those mining installations. Strong night noises, explosions, trucks and huge dust amounts are some of these people's problems. While the only systematic data that can be contested by state authorities is the particulate material (measured in PM10 particles) that can produce respiratory diseases in long periods, big mining corporations argue that there are no infractions concerning those regulations. Since two years, we settle a ground field in the region for research, observe and listening what inhabitants have to said concerning mining activities. We have found heterogeneous documents that settle Tierra Amarilla as a strongly polluted territory, with serious health problems among inhabitants. Interviews with an ethnographic approach show us how deep are those problems.

Session Organizer:

Ann Kelly, King's College London

Chair:

Diana Ojeda, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

Discussant:

Javier Lezaun, University of Oxford

287. Conspiracy Theorists and Techno-Science - I
8:00 to 9:30 am

Techno-science, and the changes wrought by techno-science, frequently result in pushback. While such resistance can be grounded in attention to risks and social justice issues, this resistance can also take the form of conspiratorial reactions. From climate change denial to anti-vaccine movements, from fears of 5G towers to UFOs, from pseudoscience to conspiracy theories—instead of settling contentious debates, the creation of techno-scientific evidence has repeatedly led to conflict over what it is that particular evidence truly shows. Not simply consisting of a rejection of techno-science, conspiracy adherents marshal government documents and scientific reports in order to push for conclusions other than those found in those materials; with many conspiracy advocates learning to skillfully deploy the language of expertise in order to bolster, and spread, their claims. This session engages with the conference theme of “good relations” by approaching the matter of relations from the opposite direction. We seek to investigate the sorts of “bad,” “inappropriate,” “conspiratorial,” or “unforeseen” relations that emerge from modes of techno-scientific expertise and knowledge making. In what ways does the same evidence get mobilized by groups with differing agendas to advance bizarre claims? How have different media technologies afforded the efficient spread of such thinking? Beyond treating them as a source purely for concern or derision, what can (or should) STS scholars learn from studying pseudoscience and conspiracy theories? Beyond an assemblage of case studies, we hope our panel will demonstrate how views that are often treated as unserious deserve serious critical attention.

Participants:

Black-boxing the Black Site: The UFO As Technoscientific Conspiracy *Kate Dorsch, The University of Pennsylvania*

A Cold War classic of conspiracy theories has seen a revival in recent years. In 2017, the New York Times reported the revelations of a secret Pentagon black money program, the Advanced Aerospace Threat Identification Program, or AATIP. The alleged object of this shadow program? The elusive unidentified flying object. What has resulted is a conspiracy of glacial proportions: slow-moving but relentless, as historically deep as it is culturally broad. Discussions both academic and conspiratorial around AATIP have concerned all angles of UFO lore, from secret government technologies to a national or global cover-up of intergalactic travelers. But what is most striking in these narratives is their historical resonance with the UFO conspiracies of the mid-20th century. Congress, the Pentagon and Department of Defense, the private aerospace/aeronautical industry, professional scientists on the payroll of the American military-industrial complex – all these forces are conspiring to keep “the truth” from you, the innocently, profoundly curious American citizen. The actors, objects, and explanations remain strikingly unchanged. The persistence over time of the UFO as an object of technoscientific conspiracy reveals the complicated nature of the American citizen to the science and technology that too often defines “first world culture.” It cuts to the core of ongoing discussions about the capacity of a democratic body to adequately debate and consult on technoscientific policy and development, and inversely the dangers of the expertise state. This paper will explore how UFO conspiracies of both the past and present reveal ongoing challenges in public understanding of science and science communication, and the role of the “expert” – professional or experiential – in democratic participation and deliberation.

Catastrophic Code – Y2K as Computerized Conspiracy *Zachary M Loeb, History & Sociology of Science, University of Pennsylvania*

With the deadline of December 31, 1999 less than a year away, the Senate’s Special Report on Y2K warned that much work remained. Though the report’s assessment was presented in measured tones, for some Y2K watchers the report was still overly optimistic. Thus, the Y2K catastrophist Gary North derided the report as “exactly what the public wants to hear,” warning that Y2K represented a potential “catastrophe on a scale

undreamed of as recently as 1995.” North was only one of many individuals who believed that Y2K would be disastrous, regardless of the assurances by computer professionals and government agencies that the problem would be fixed. Though many of these figures drew upon religious scripture to bolster their grim predictions, just as many of these Y2K catastrophists analyzed news reports, carefully poured over Congressional testimony, and highlighted the warnings circulating within the IT community. Thus, Y2K catastrophists and conspiracy theorists, consistently drew upon the information created by technological experts in order to support their own claims, repeatedly couching eschatological beliefs in the technical terminology of IT professionals. While Y2K is often remembered as something of a hoax ginned up by doomsayers, this paper will consider the ways in which those doomsayers drew upon the work of technical and scientific experts to make their claims.

Future Proves Past: The “Q Clock” and Instruments of Conspiracy *Alice Marwick, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill; William Clyde Partin, Data & Society Research Institute*

Recently, STS scholars have debated the relationship between the symmetry principle, right-wing populism, and the (so-called) “post-truth” in Western societies. Our paper contributes to this debate with a detailed case study of knowledge production in the QAnon conspiracy, which positions Donald Trump against an elite cabal of pedophiles. While QAnon incorporates many conspiratorial tropes, it alone centers on a series of posts, or “Drops,” by “Q” – supposedly a Trump administration insider – which challenge readers to research and decode them. Adherents consider these Drops to be infallible and, if correctly interpreted, to predict future geopolitical events or provide interpretive closure on past ones. The combination of a counterfactual conspiracy, a knowledge-making apparatus, and an appendage of right-wing populism makes QAnon particularly useful for assessing STS debates about post-truth. We draw on months of non-participant observation and archival work to describe how Qanon researchers utilize an interpretive instrument called the “QClock” to augment their research and validate the authenticity of Q’s Drops. The QClock is an elaborate graphic subdivided into 30 temporal axes; researchers situate a given Drop on one axis and the Clock draws relationships to other, supposedly relevant Drops. We argue that the QClock recasts coincidental relationships as providential, proving the authenticity of Q’s Drops and the legitimacy of the conspiracy overall. Ultimately, our findings lend credence to the idea that, while knowledge may always be “otherwise,” it still requires incentives, infrastructures, efforts, and validation structures to take root, even and especially when it comes to conspiracy theories.

Taxonomizing Conspiratorial Information Practices: Examining the Ong’s Hat Legend *James A Hodges, The University of Texas at Austin*

This paper examines an influential hoax within the sphere of amateur online science in order to understand the ways that alternative epistemic communities engage with institutionally recognized scientific literature in idiosyncratic ways while advancing epistemological viewpoints frequently denigrated as “conspiracy theories.” Rather than attempting to judge the veracity or the merit of such theories, I instead build on Latour and Woolgar’s (1979) suggestion that factuality is constructed during a series of negotiations between material conditions and human actors. In the process, I develop a preliminary taxonomy of the information practices that conspiracy theorists use. The case study is drawn from the urban legend of “Ong’s Hat,” which suggests that a group of Princeton University-affiliated physicists developed techniques for inter-dimensional travel in the 1980s. The theory developed a wide enough online following that it was discussed on nationally syndicated conspiracy radio and served as the subject of at least one academic monograph (Kinsella

2011). More recently, Ong's Hat has been reframed as a predecessor for the online QAnon movement (Hon 2020). The study examines the Ong's Hat Incunabula catalog, a "brochure" advertising both real and fabricated publications central in the Ong's Hat legend. First, I quantify and classify both the authentic and fabricated sources listed in this catalog according to meaningful characteristics, focusing on their relationships to institutionally recognized scientific literature. Next, I note the specific narrative function of each publication in order to develop a taxonomy of conspiracist information practices. Latour, B., & Woolgar, S. (1979). *Laboratory Life: The Construction of Scientific Facts*. Princeton University Press. Hon, A. (2020, August 2). What ARGs Can Teach Us About QAnon. <https://mssv.net/2020/08/02/what-args-can-teach-us-about-qanon/> Kinsella, M. (2011). *Legend-tripping online supernatural folklore and the search for Ong's hat*. University Press of Mississippi.

Session Organizers:

Zachary M Loeb, History & Sociology of Science, University of Pennsylvania

Kate Dorsch, The University of Pennsylvania

288. **Becoming with Water: Ethnographic and Methodological Reconfigurations — III**

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

How do efforts for sustainability view water? What technologies emerge as commercial and financial sectors become entangled with oceanic worlds and riverine landscapes? This panel engages with an ever-expanding capitalocene's quests for managing, modifying and moderating water. Consequently, architectures of extraction emerge in dialogue with water and its properties. Using these very technologies as sites of rethinking theory and methodological approaches, the authors of this panel invite attention to the ways in which water becomes with infrastructures, sustainability and finance. Rather than think with trends in STS that question the limitations of technoscientific modernities, this panel opens up new ways of conceptualizing the technocratic. It illustrates that water is internal to the very making of the operations that seek to control it.

Participants:

Chasing Waves: Making Sense of the Interaction Between Offices and Waters in The Blue Economy *Aneil Tripathy*

For the past six years I have conducted fieldwork in sustainable and climate finance with a focus on the experiences of people working in this sector and the nature of their white collar work in this sector. I am now beginning research on the blue economy to understand how this field of finance symbolically and materially grounded in ocean and water management intersects with the climate finance world I have studied. The blue economy is a growing discourse amongst policymakers and financiers centred on ocean and water management and commercial activity. Through focusing on a Republic of the Seychelles bond connected to funding marine conservation I both connect to and challenge my knowledge of and fieldwork in climate finance offices to the direct environmental and social impacts of a bond associated with climate finance and the blue economy. I begin here with an analysis of the data, infographics and water images through which my climate finance interlocutors interact with water and notions of the blue economy. These images and words that appear in reports, PowerPoints, and in online conferences, are the primary medium through which my interlocutors encounter and make sense of water systems and conceptualize the blue economy. Through making sense of the encounter of water, data and people at this point in the blue economy, I create space to connect this field to future fieldwork at beaches, marine zones, and in waters associated with the numbers and images encountered by my climate finance interlocutors.

Artificial Paradise: An Investigation of Oceanic and More-Than-Human Afterlife in Hong Kong's Archipelago *Marie*

Lecuyer, Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA)

Burials have taken an "oceanic" (analog and digital) turn in Hong Kong's archipelago. Newly delimited marine cemeteries for humans have appeared alongside oceanic dead zones where non-human life has withered, while web platforms now host the dead into new "ether worlds" that gods are sometimes said to originally inhabit. The project navigates into ocean-based funerary architecture and designs by asking: How do architects and designers imagine the future of death in Hong Kong? How does their concern for human death intersect with ecological death? And how does the "oceanization" and potential "dissipation" of death reconfigure Chinese animist practices of worshipping? To address the new materializations, and in fact the possible dissolution, of memory and its haunting potentialities, I build on the spectral turn in anthropology as well as from a media ecological approach. By so doing, I apprehend the notion of spectrality as a past-oriented afterlife form, as well as in physical terms, as a future-oriented and transductive phenomenon whose propagation through media creates potential haunting. This allows me to further consider the role of watery media ("natural" and technological) in the writing, archiving or erasing of death and life trajectories, and its role in the propagation of potentially neoliberal imaginaries. The project sounds out potential spectres by taking on a spectral, or infra-linguistic, methodology. This involves multimedia ethnography of online and offline participant observation in non/conventional cemeteries and among the main actors of the death-care industry.

Water, work and mineralisation: three gold mining organisations in Busia, Uganda *Esther van de Camp, Leiden University*

Within current transformations to sustainability (T2S) trends, it seems ever more challenging to understand artisanal and small-scale gold mining (ASGM) as a viable source of income and employment, now or in the future. Categorical problematisations of the sector can – and have been – harmful and make no sense; ASGM provides livelihoods for millions of people and is highly diverse. A growing body of literature argues that a vertical view and socio-nature approach are necessary to situate and understand mining and miners. Building on this vertical turn – recently taken in anthropology, geography and STS – this paper aims to draw attention, underground, to the water in the mines. Water finds the weak parts in the ground to move through, this can be in soil, rock or vein. The case of three neighbouring Artisanal and Small-scale Mining Organisations (ASMOs) demonstrates how water both connects their work and differentiates the materiality of their workplaces. Exploring the relations between work, water and minerals, this paper draws from PhD research on transformation and sustainability in ASGM in Busia, Uganda. An interdisciplinary approach includes research methods from both industrial ecology and anthropology: participatory observation, semi-structured interviews, transect walks, life cycle assessment (LCA) and scenario planning. Ethnographic fieldwork took place in July-October 2019 and January-March 2020 – additional research will be conducted digitally or in Busia depending on developments around COVID-19.

Tinkering (infra)structures: a feminist analysis of a wastewaterscape in Maharashtra, India *Irene Leonardelli, IHE Delft Institute for Water Education; Jeltsje Kemerink-Seyoum, IHE Delft Institute for Water Education*

The Purandar Lift Irrigation Scheme is a piece of infrastructure that transports wastewater from the city of Pune (Maharashtra, India) to a drought prone rural area where farmers use it for irrigation. The scheme is part of the efforts of the Government of Maharashtra to address water scarcity, while encouraging farmers to shift from cultivating traditional rain-fed crops to cultivating commercial crops. In this paper, we focus on one of the villages served by this infrastructure to study how a wastewaterscape

emerges. Firstly, we focus on acts of sociotechnical tinkering to unfold how different actors (farmers, engineers, field officers) exercise their agency to shape materially and politically the infrastructure. We show how these acts often deviate and exceed formal technical designs, policies and regulations. Yet we are also inspired by a definition of agency that takes into consideration more-than-human actors –including (waste)water, soil, technology- to bring further nuance to more structural, or tautological analyses of how water infrastructures work and wastewaterscapes emerge. In the second part of this paper, we show how different human and more-than-human actors relate within and rearrange the wastewaterscape often in unexpected ways that subtly challenge power hierarchies (in our case, those based on gender and caste) and/or evade human intentionality. Inspired by feminist scholars, we show how tinkering can become a useful theoretical and methodological tool to go beyond the agency-structure binary; to tease out complexity and to study water infrastructures, but also water governance and processes of agrarian in a critical and political manner.

Session Organizer:

Dana Burton, George Washington University

Chair:

Shweta Krishnan, George Washington University

289. Logics of anticipation I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

TBD

Participants:

“Ambiguity Of Harm”: Technology, Disasters, And Governance *Malika Older, School for Future of Innovation in Society, Arizona State University*

The unfolding of the COVID-19 pandemic response offers a dichotomy of approaches: on the one hand, cutting-edge science and large amounts of money thrown behind the development of vaccines and therapeutics; on the other, efforts to stop the transmission of the disease by changing behaviors, either by government fiat, voluntary adhesion, or some combination (lockdowns, masks, and social distancing). This illustrates some of the common interactions of disasters and technology.

Technology is often held up as the one-stop solution to all sorts of disaster response problems, from communications to seawalls. The financial dynamics of disaster response often prioritize expensive, visible projects over less apparent initiatives like skills-building or community organizing. The pernicious myth that the virus was engineered in a lab reflects the toxic effects of technological disasters. Meanwhile, governments have struggled to articulate their precise role, the minimums and the limits of their responsibilities, leaving an uncertainty that has toxic effects on communities (Kroll-Smith and Couch, 1990; Older 2019). Improving our preparedness, response, and ability to learn from disasters requires significant reorientation in how we perceive disasters, technology, and governance. This paper will interrogate the ambiguous, technologically inflected responsibilities of governments during disaster response, building on previous work (Older, 2019) that applied findings about the corrosive effects of technological disasters (Freudenburg, 1997) to disaster responses. It asks the question: what are the relationships that could help us better prepare for and deal with disasters, and how can technology support instead of hindering them?

Covid-19 as a slow disaster: an STS perspective as intervention in the management of the pandemic. *Israel Rodriguez-Giralt, Fundació per la Universitat Oberta de Catalunya*

This talk aims to “think with” the intense adventure in which I have been involved. It tells the story of a multidisciplinary Technical Support Group (TSG) on the Catalan government's pandemic. This particular task force was aimed to contribute to “everything necessary to understand and get involved in the logic

of this epidemic”. This included epidemiological surveillance issues, health prevention and preparedness, working at the healthcare and community level or adding risk communication and citizen involvement. For about 4 months, this multidisciplinary team of 8 people worked intensively to develop ideas, technical documents and tools for risk communication, protocols, indicators, alert plans, social support strategies for isolation and quarantine... Ethnographically, I am interested in reflecting upon two interconnected processes: 1) the role and boundary-work of epidemiology throughout the pandemic, interrogating whether the pandemic is changing the field of practice and/or its academic status, particularly concerning other disciplines and medical specialities, and 2) in what way, this interpellates and intertwines with our own capacities/incapacities, as social scientists, especially as STS scholars, to collaborate and be relevant in the midst of a pandemic. In particular, I will reflect upon the notion of “slow disaster” and how it has worked in our TSG as a boundary-concept that has had enough immutable content to maintain integrity and facilitate communication despite being understood in different ways across various experts and publics. In this regard, the notion has become an interesting, and still intriguing, way of negotiating my expertise, as a social scientist, and mostly as “disasterologist”, to intervene in the conceptual and practical articulation of the pandemic.

Planning to Make Do: Improvisation in Nuclear Emergency Response *Sonja Schmid, Virginia Tech, Falls Church; Davide Orsini, Rachel Carson Center, LMU Munich*

Emergency response in the nuclear sector—like in other sectors—is the end tale of complex risk assessment practices with distinct historical trajectories. In this paper we use emergency response planning documents and interviews with experts to examine how different countries have approached the problem of nuclear emergency preparedness and response. In particular, we focus on the role of improvisation and how such action is shaped by infrastructures, epistemic traditions, and organizational cultures. Building on previous research in organization studies and disaster sociology, we argue that improvisation is not “freelancing” but a bounded activity defined by the aforementioned factors and by a (more or less) explicit acknowledgment of the limits of forecasting (e.g. Bigley and Roberts, 2001). What are the prerequisites for an effective use of flexible interventions to cope with unforeseen consequences of accidents? So far, studies of improvisation in emergency response have mostly focused on organizational and individual cognitive capacities in dealing with unprecedented events. An STS oriented analysis should aim at reintroducing broader cultural and contextual factors into the equation, including (but not limited to) the regulatory environment, knowledge cultures, and the challenging issue of liability. Finally, we examine the tensions between national emergency response traditions and international response organizations. How could an international response team operate in different national scenarios, keeping in mind different comfort levels of engaging in expert improvisation?

Session Organizer:

Sonja Schmid, Virginia Tech, Falls Church

290. Splinternets - I: Concepts

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Participants:

Mesh Networks: Strategic Frictions and Local Circulations *Rory Solomon, The New School*

Network theory has traditionally argued that the potency of digital communication infrastructures lies in their capacity to connect. (Castells 1996, Galloway 2004, Benkler 2006) Taking the virtue of connectivity as axiomatic, much scholarship has expressed consternation over the degree to which the internet has

become like a shopping mall, comprised of “privately owned, publicly accessible” walled gardens (Chun 2008), raising alarm about the degree to which the internet has lost sight of its original promise of global interconnectivity at risk of succumbing to Balkanized “splinternets.” (Morozov 2010, Malcomson 2016) This paper takes these concerns seriously but considers efforts in response that embrace strategic frictions rather than seamlessness by examining mesh networks: a class of digital communications infrastructure reticulated through physical peer-to-peer links, championed as a community-oriented, decentralized alternative to traditional grid-based apparatus. Mesh activists enact networking practices as situated knowledge (Haraway 1988) negotiating protocols and policies that attend to the specificities of community concern, sometimes even celebrating local-only digital networks, disconnected from global circulations, as techniques to inoculate the local from infrastructural encroachments of multinational technology corporations. Sharing findings from ethnographic research working with mesh network developers over the last four years, I show that these technology activists compel us to consider that powerful network players actually generate profound disconnectivities, to which their seamless, ubiquitous data flows are presented as solution: connectivity as pharmakon, poison and cure. Community network activists, enmeshed in the local, offer a model for leveraging the power of splintering to renegotiate interoperability on our own terms.

The Splinternet That Always Was: Licklider And Baran In Conflict *Daniel Nemenyi, King's College London*

This paper theoretically problematizes the notion that the internet was at its invention a unifying force, one which has gradually fragmented into ‘splinternets’. It posits that at the outset of the internet there were two opposing concepts of what constitutes an inter-network: a topological one and an epistemological one. The discourse of the internet’s historical fracturing emerges from the former, which conceives of that which joins networks as being their topological connection to one another. This topological model has become the conventional mode for thinking about what makes the internet more than a simple network, and conversely what makes the internet divisible into ‘splinternets’ as topological connections break down. What I call the ‘epistemological’ model conceives of that which constitutes the unifying force of the internetwork as being not the connection of networks, but their conflict over one another’s knowledge. Internets are constituted through cryptological conflicts over access, and entropic conflicts over disinformation. At stake in this epistemological model of an internet -- ontologically not merely historically -- is the control of one network over another. Two figures from early-internet history figure these two models. J. C. R. Licklider, conceiving of the internet as the ‘interconnection’ of ‘communities of geographically separated people’ represents the standard topological concept. And Paul Baran, whose survivable and, significantly, encrypted network represents the epistemological. My paper will explore these two opposing concepts of internet -- and their derivative ‘splinternets’ -- historically by means of Licklider and Baran’s opposing thought.

Trust, Risk, and Transitivity: On Trustworthy Computing as Network, Assemblage, and Infrastructure *Ashwin Jacob Mathew, King's College London*

Trust and risk are central problems for our times, whether in discussions about living in “risk societies”, or about how to ensure trust in political institutions. Trust is often viewed in relation to risk, as a means for allowing potentially risky actions to proceed - for example, by managing risks in assembling the disparate social and technological components that compose global computing infrastructures, such as the Internet. In this paper, I present a comparative analysis of trust and risk, placing the conventional relational account into conversation with distinctive characteristics that become clear when considering

trust and risk in the context of sociotechnical systems. I draw from a range of perspectives on trustworthy computing to argue for two critical differences between trust and risk that have significant implications for thinking about their relationship. First, that risk is transitive, while trust is intransitive - which is to say that risk travels across sociotechnical systems, while trust does not. Second, that risk is sociomaterial and sociotechnical, while trust is always and only social - which is to say that risk is recognised and embedded through interlocking social, material, and technological elements, while trust depends entirely upon social interaction, with no potential for material or technological supports. My argument suggests that it is a shared recognition of risk that holds sociotechnical systems together, which calls for responses that cannot be limited to trust alone, drawing from broader social, material, and technological mechanisms that enable cooperation.

Session Organizer:

Ashwin Jacob Mathew, King's College London

Discussant:

Elisa Oreglia, King's College London

291. Interrogating STS as Critical Pedagogy I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

In Summer 2021, the NSF-funded ‘STS as a Critical Pedagogy Workshop’ occurred over four separate online sessions, with approximately 35 participants, primarily from the United States. This panel presents papers from participants in the workshop that reflect on practices of teaching and learning STS across a variety of domains, from engineering to art & media, both inside higher ed and beyond. These papers offer novel ways of conceptualizing and implementing critical STS pedagogies even as they interrogate what STS as critical pedagogy might mean.

Participants:

Where is the Nonhuman in Sociotechnical Engineering Education?: Post Constructivist STS for and in Engineering Education *Elizabeth A. Reddy, Colorado School Of Mines*

Critical engineering education posits engineering as a “sociotechnical” activity. Training students to be sensitive to the entanglements of technologies and social factors has been an important pedagogical move for engineering educators and a crucial issue as attention to climate change and careful intervention into global politics of knowledge are made central to engineering practice. However, this framing is not entirely satisfactory to some STS and environmental humanities scholars. Environmental conditions, forces, and agents are critical to consider in relation to technologies, too. As historian Sara Pritchard summarizes these contemporary movements, they are sensitive to the social, the technical, and the environmental as situated, co-produced, and mutually interdependent fields of knowledge and action, though doing so means grappling with “complicated, dialectical dynamics among all three factors simultaneously” (2014:231). In this paper, I explore where a framework of “sociotechnical” action may fall short of decentering old models of anthropocentrism that frame mainstream ideologies around technology for engineers in formation. I also consider how “sociotechnical” language may obscure more radical work of engineering education. In this way, I seek to explore the poetics and pragmatics of what Hannah Knox and Tone Huse (2015) have called post constructivist STS scholarship in engineering education today. S. B. Pritchard, 2014 “Toward an Environmental History of Technology” in A. C. Isenberg, Ed., Oxford Handbook of Environmental History. Oxford: Oxford University Press. H. Knox and T. Huse. 2015 “Political Materials : Rethinking Environment , Remaking Theory.” *Distinktion: Scandinavian Journal of Social Theory* 16, no. 1: 1–16.

STS as a Critical Pedagogy through Moments of Technological Failure, Breakdown, and Troubles *Ann Wu, University of*

Texas at Dallas

As digital media making becomes increasingly popularized in classrooms, art and media educators are faced with not only mastering digital technologies for curricular planning but also improvising with these disobedient objects during pedagogical exchanges (Delacruz, 2004; Black, J., & Browning, 2011). Drawing from my five-weeks action research project teaching video game modifications for social justice with teens in a US public library setting, this paper examines repeated moments of technological failures, breakdowns, and troubles during teaching practice. Instead of interpreting these glitches as pedagogical setbacks, I argue that these everyday happenings are sites for practicing STS as a critical pedagogy. In theorizing critical pedagogy, Paulo Freire argued that “education as the practice of freedom” (p. 81) needs to be predicated upon a dialogic exchange through problem-posing. In the context of teaching with and through digital technologies, the problems posed by these technological failures become grounds for those involved in the pedagogical encounter “to perceive critically the way they exist in the world with which and in which they find themselves” (p. 83). As Benjamin (2019) argued, moments of technological failures provide “powerful opportunities to examine the overall system” (p. 24) as they expose the various inner logics of “default discrimination” (p. 55) enacted by technologies when they’re working smoothly. These moments, then, can be understood as invitations for educators to probe the previously unnoticeable logics of these technologies, and in return practice and exercise negotiating our respective agencies and boundaries with these technologies. References: Benjamin, R. (2019). *Race after technology: Abolitionist tools for the new jim code*. Cambridge, UK: Polity Press. Black, J., & Browning, K. (2011). Creativity in digital art education teaching practices. *Art Education*, 64(5), 19-34. Delacruz, E. (2004). Teachers' working conditions and the unmet promise of technology. *Studies in Art Education*, 46(1), 6-19. Freire, P. (1970/2011). *Pedagogy of the oppressed*. New York, NY: Continuum.

On STS and Critical Feminism Pedagogy: Repair and Reconnection in Community Data *Anita Say Chan, University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign*

Feminist science and technology studies scholars have argued for alternative pathways to generate potentials for remaking worlds. Alongside global studies scholars, they argue for the need to foster “new arts of noticing” (Tsing 2015) and a “staying with the trouble” (Haraway 2016) that could specifically allow researchers to get outside dominant frameworks and tempos of modernity around progress. This paper thus shares perspectives from one US public university’s campus-based design - The Community Data Clinic at the University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign - in efforts to foster “new arts of noticing” via an interdisciplinary pedagogy and lab engagements exploring other means for recognizing value and possibility in patient tempos, local scales, and non-forward motion. Acting as research collaborators with a local civic organizations’ data analysis efforts, the clinic’s engagements explore what new forms of value feminist qualitative research methods and analysis techniques can bring in dialogue with local civic network’ growing efforts to leverage data infrastructures and expand data methods. Centering new frames for patience, review and reconsideration, local situatedness over global scale, and reconnectedness over efficiency, as assets for responsible and accountable community data practice, the lab centers engagements with a local data actors and stewards - rather than large data-driven corporations that “big data” has tended to “fetishize” (Crawford and boyd 2014) - to reveal “new arts of noticing” in research methods.

Queer possibilities in/through teaching science communication *Eleanor Armstrong, University of Delaware; Simon Lock, University College London*

Unpicking teaching the positions/interactions of scientists, science communicators, and publics in a science communication module has encouraged us to explore the queer possibility in reconfiguring our pedagogy in the classroom. Using elements of our module redevelopment to guide the paper, we will explore how queer approaches to this work can expand the content, delivery, and classroom practice. We use the paper expansively about queer pedagogy, and how methodological situatedness can change our educative work in the academy.

Session Organizer:

Emily York, James Madison University

Discussant:

Marisa R Brandt, Michigan State University

292. What we talk about when we talk about depth – I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 *Virtual*: 23

Recent scholarship on mining and drilling, urban infrastructure, maritime logistics, the transit of toxins, the anthropocene, and the disposal of bodies theorizes the politics of sub-surface worlds (Anand 2017, Appel et al. 2015, Campling & Colás 2021, Klinger 2017, Murphy 2013, Yusoff 2018). Bringing these depths into view has centered new spaces, scales, materials, and relations. Yet the concept of depth itself, and the responsibilities that attend its investigation, have not been sufficiently examined. Depth is more than a simple spatial signifier or linguistic trope. Thinking with and beyond verticality (Graham and Hewitt 2012), volumetric space (Weizman 2007, Elden 2013, Billé 2018), and metaphor (McKittrick 2018, Shalem 2017), we want to suggest that the deeps constitute a semiotic landscape that is resolutely material but always exceeds conventional materialist readings. Deep spaces matter: they are simultaneously material and meaningful. This panel engages critically and creatively with the mattering of chthonic landscapes, defined broadly. Encoded in the concept of depth are all kinds of latent associations and meanings. As such, we may speak of deep time, deep sleep, deep ecology, deep learning, the deep state, skin deep, diving deep, depth of character, depth of perception, depth of field, depth of meaning, etc. How, we ask, are these (and many other) conceptualizations of depth tied to the deep places of the earth? And if, as Spivak teaches us, thought must be “written on the planet as planet” (2012: 349), how does thinking operate beneath the planetary surface?

Participants:

A Broad Now: Engaging the speculative present on the Salar de Atacama *Anna Friz, University of California, Santa Cruz*
A significant portion of the world’s lithium is mined in the Salar de Atacama in Chile, which was once the bottom of a sea and which contains rare geologic and organic systems. This high altitude desert includes the “Valle de la Luna” and “Valle de Marte”, so named because of their similarity to lunar or off-worldly landscapes and geology—the Mars Rover and other unmanned Mars modules have been tested here. The extractivist logic that developed and sustains the massive mining operations in Atacama that continue to radically reshape the desert is also the framework that drives imminent plans for future extra-planetary operations envisioned by today’s billionaires on the moon or on Mars. My radio art work and associated audio-visual installation “Salar” seek to de-totalize such narratives around the Atacama desert in favour of a “many worlds” (Blaser and de la Cadena, 2018) approach to land, space and temporality. “Salar” explores geological history, changes of state such as evaporation, sociocultural imaginaries, industry and the interplay between off-world futures and this-worldly possibility. My approach to fieldwork and resulting media art works rejects the persistent colonial narratives of wasteland/wasted land that are employed to justify indiscriminate mining operations in this often harsh but vital desert environment. What I am defining as a ‘broad now’ frames human endeavour in the desert in a non-linear fashion and in opposition to the futurism proposed by industries working at the so-called cutting edge of mechanization and systems innovation. A broad now reconsiders the human scale of activity

within the temporality of geological time, such that 'now' includes all the time(s) of human presence in the desert. The work does not try to replace one future with another, but to undermine such a deterministic future in favour of a surplus of present; delving more deeply into this expanded conception of the present to recognize other relationships and ways of being. The shifting states of wet and dry or hard and soft leave traces upon the land and reveal the interplay between underground, underwater, surface and air. Engaging with forces of perceptual uncertainty characteristic of the desert--such as the prevalence of mirage, the ambiguity of sounds and their sources, and the difficulty in judging distances--my media works reflect upon experience in the desert of what is far and near in space and time. I seek to expand what counts as 'now' by documenting the accumulation of evidence of human presence, life, labour and industry in this area together with extra-human processes operating at the speeds of geological change or weathering.

How Dangers (Should) Re-emerge From the Aquatic Abyss *Sven Bergmann, German Maritime Museum*

Water is good to think with because it allows to challenge land-centered ideas. Therefore, the seemingly infinite size and depth of the ocean has long led to the ocean being conceived as a vast and eternal sink for objects and substances. In contrast, the rise in sea level or the appearance of microplastics can be understood as a particular response from the depths of the ocean towards this "slow violence". Drawing on research in the EU project "North Sea Wrecks" that investigates the contamination of naval wrecks and munitions, I propose to discuss some rather unarticulated dimensions of depth. For a long time, munitions sunk by warfare or dumped after war were only a problem when they affected shipping routes or the offshore projects; otherwise they were rather invisible (and not present in most people's everyday life). Moreover, in the current scientific discussion on deep-water munitions, the context of war hardly receives any attention. While the naval wrecks and the sailors who sank with the ships lie in the depths, forming sea graves and artificial reefs, after decades, hazardous TNT leaks out of the corroding shells and torpedoes; creating both uncertain and indeterminate environmental conditions. In my presentation, I will problematize the ambiguity of depth in this project. I will argue that by focusing on depth and abyss, interesting semiotic-material interconnections and entanglements are salvaged, but also voids of the subject emerge. It is precisely these unarticulated positions that prevent us from caring about waste and residues of wars.

Deep learning in the planetary oilfield: On subterranean plasticity *John Kendall, U Minnesota*

Oilfield development is becoming more technologically complex, its financing more widely distributed across capital markets, and its products more integral to global political economy. It is not just that oil demand continues to rise but, more critically, that the oilfield has moved in lockstep with the 'green', high-tech, data-driven economy ostensibly supposed to supersede it. Indeed, like Arbodela's "planetary mine," the oilfield of late industrialization is a meshwork of spatial technologies, territorial infrastructures, and bodies conditioning the very possibility of so-called 'postindustrial' capitalist society. More to the point of this paper, it is this reformatting of the oilfield which has allowed the industry to not merely survive but capitalize on cutting-edge information and communications technologies for the sake of extracting otherwise irretrievable oil. This synergy has mutated the conditions of intelligibility of the oilfield itself. Predictive data analytics like artificial neural networks can only be useful for extraction if they presuppose a concept of the oilfield as something reducible to the datasets used to model it. For them to predict anything, the oilfield cannot be regarded as some hidden, uncertain interiority discovered in the slow process of surveying, drilling, and extracting but instead, it must be treated as if it is the historical data abstracted from other oilfields. Both the ontological apriority of the oilfield and the spatiotemporal delay

of its intelligibility are therefore refused. The oilfield becomes something virtual, plastic, and protean—characteristics which together compose a concept of the oilfield adequate to its increasingly volatile, relentless extraction.

The Plume: movement and mixture in subterranean water worlds *Andrea Ballestero, University of Southern California*

As hydrogeologists convey the depth of fluid dynamics to publics, they resort to a variety of models: physical, conceptual and mathematical. Often organized as public exhibitions, these events are carefully staged and give experts the opportunity to manipulate artifacts, compose stories, and invite their audiences to speculate about what happens deep below the surface. This paper examines how one conceptual model, "the plume," emerges as a prominent figure to understand the fragility of aquifers in the context of water exploitation and saline intrusion in coastal Costa Rica. By focusing on the history of the plume as a scientific figure and on its social life among everyday citizens, I make three points. First, I examine the peculiar mixture that the plume is, a fluid moving through another, mixing, but at a scale that keeps the difference between the two alive. Second, I show how subterranean structures are inflected with movement, thereby challenging the static imaginaries that dominate our investigations of the underground's "inhuman" character. Finally, by noting mixture and movement, I show how subterranean water disrupts dichotomous oppositions between above and below the surface histories.

Session Organizers:

Anya Kaplan-Seem, University of Minnesota

Xander Lenc, University of California, Berkeley

Nicholas Anderman, University of California, Berkeley

Chair:

Nicholas Anderman, University of California, Berkeley

293. Technology Needs of the Muslim Communities Around the World

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Participants:

A Digital Ethnographic Study Of Online Ramadan and Digital Muslim Community: What changed for Muslims? *Niloufar Hajirahimikalhroudi*

For most Muslims Ramadan is the month of community and gatherings. Since the pandemic, COVID19 restrictions turned Ramadan's offline celebration into online events. Muslim Community was innovative in adopting the technologies into their community practices during Ramadan and this all happened while certain media outlets raised questions regarding how Muslims tackle with COVID19 restriction during Ramadan and judged the community's practices one-sided. In this research, through digital ethnography, the researcher looks at the communication technology and media's role in empowering the Muslim community's practices. Digital ethnography enables the researcher to get as close as possible to the experience of the Muslim community and their online presence. The focus of this paper is on how online platforms and technologies during Ramadans of 2020 and 2021 enable the diasporic young Muslims to feel a sense of belonging in the European context and practice cultural citizenship. The findings of the studies until this point are promising that the online environment has enabled the diversity of Muslims to self-represent themselves. Young Muslims practiced their leadership in an online Ramadan and they tried to deconstruct the power structures from their inner circles.

Assisted Reproductive Technologies in the Islamic Republic: Infertility, Inequality and Masculinities in Iran *Tara Asgarilaleh, University of Cambridge*

This research examines how (in)fertile couples, men in particular,

can access and utilize assisted reproductive technologies (ARTs) in the socio-cultural, legal, religious and medical context of contemporary Iran. Iran is the only Muslim country in which ARTs, including the use of donor gametes and embryos, have been partly regulated by the state through the recent Increasing Population Policies, and more significantly, have been widely legitimized by religious authorities. Although the state partly subsidizes ARTs, they are not equally accessible to all. In Iran, infertility—a stigmatized condition—is considered a ‘woman’s problem’; male infertility is hardly recognized or discussed in families, society, or the social sciences. This ethnographic study will yield insights into male infertility and the use of ARTs in Iran and how this relates to dominant notions of masculinity. It will build on four core theoretical notions—‘reproductive navigation’, ‘(Islamic) biopolitics’, ‘stratified reproduction’ and ‘emerging masculinities’—and take an intersectional perspective considering gender, class and religion. For the purpose of 4S Conference, I will present a critical review of the literature on masculinities and Iranian ARTs. I will show how in conversation with the literature I designed my study, in particular, at the times of COVID-19. I began with my empirical research in autumn 2021 which is building on months of initial contacts and my previous research on similar topic in Iran. The research methods includes: observations of online platforms used and shared by (in)fertile couples; interviews with couples, religious authorities, medical professionals and policymakers.

Israel Genome Project: How Genetics Reaffirms National Identity And Idea Of Citizenship *Premi Devi*

Israel is a country in the middle east with a population of over 8.6 million. More than 74 percent are Jews, around 20 percent are Arabs. Geographically it is significant to note that it shares boundaries with Lebanon, Syria, Palestine, and Jordan. Israel has also seen many migrants settling in its territory in recent times. However, only Jewish ancestry wins Israeli citizenship. Israel needs to be at the edge of every new development in science and technology to sustain and growth of their society in a country full of unforgiving deserts. The institutionalization of science and technology and a culture of innovation and entrepreneurialism has made the country one of the leading hubs for start-ups. It is the second-highest spending on Research and Development as a percentage of its GDP in the world. The new science of biotechnology serves to fulfill almost all their national aspirations. Apart from being a holy land for Abrahamic religions, the history of the region and its population is often contested. It is a narrative that is co-constructed through conventional sources of history but also archaeology. Indeed, the latter has also challenged the former on various counts. Does a genetic account of the past challenge the popular narratives of Israel’s history?

mtDNA Tests as a Vehicle for Jewish Recognition *Yael Hashiloni-Dolev, Ben-Gurion University of the Negev; Nurit Kirsh, The Open University of Israel*

Until recently, in Israeli rabbinic discourse as well as Israeli state policy, Jewish identity was not reckoned via genetics. While academic studies looked for genetic similarities among Jewish communities, these similarities did not determine Jewishness or state policy. This study spotlights the novel use of mtDNA testing in order to determine the Jewishness of Israeli citizens who immigrated to Israel from the Former Soviet Union (FSU) 1990 onward. These tests offered by the Israeli State Rabbinate, are accompanied by heated political and religious wrangles, in particular between leaders of the Ultra-Orthodox Jewish community and the political party claiming to represent immigrants from the FSU. We aim to understand this current debate on determining Jewishness by mtDNA. We examine the reciprocal relationship between science, religion, communal identity and state policy, and question the possible social implications. In contrast to claims that the change in Jewish definition is guided by science and technology, we argue that this

change is dictated primarily by specific historical and socio-political circumstances. Furthermore, enthusiasm or rejection of the use of mtDNA for Jewish recognition depends on inclusive or exclusive ideologies, not on the indecisive content of science or religion themselves.

Session Organizer:

Firaz Peer, University Of Kentucky

294. The Boundaries of Universality – Contemporary Engagements of Science I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

In recent years, the idea that science represents universal facts has been challenged from a variety of perspectives. While scientific approaches remain a compelling and normative force in people’s ways of thinking, acting and feeling in the world, disparate alliances from across the political spectrum – anti-vaxxers, climate-change sceptics, Covid-19 deniers, but also movements informed by postcolonial critique – fundamentally call into question the status of science and its claims to universality. Today, it is necessary to ask not only “whose science”, where, and for whom, but also to investigate how people engage, or resist science’s universality. In this panel, we investigate contemporary political mobilizations with, for, and against science in fields as varied as astronomy, biomedicine, psychology, genetics, field biology, and artificial intelligence. Specifically, we are interested in the boundaries of science and the limits to its universal applicability. When, and around which issues, does universality become mobilized and contested? What are the politics behind specific attempts to universalize and/or localize knowledge? Where do claims to universality enact inclusive and/or exclusive socialities? The papers in this panel deal with the “boundary work” of science as it moves through, and is modified in, different contexts. Our common assumption is that science’s universality is not absolute, but contingent and relational. What counts as science, or as universal, is always enacted and negotiated in practice. Anthropological exploration of the mutability and mobility of universalizing and localizing dynamics in the sciences offers valuable perspectives for reflections on our own scientific practices.

Participants:

Locating Genetic Diagnostics in India *Samiksha Bhan, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology*

Global health initiatives and public private partnerships in healthcare have led to an expansion of point-of-care diagnostic tests designed to provide quick diagnoses. Especially in low- and middle-income countries, where laboratory conditions are sparse and access to diagnostic services low, portable medical devices have been celebrated, bringing into effect a “testing revolution” (Street 2018). In India, such global health initiatives have been a fertile ground for expanding genetic diagnosis in the service of public health needs. Common genetic diseases have been medicalized in health policies and at-risk populations have been identified at a time when automated devices such as PCR machines and genetic sequencers are being pushed into the global supply chain of diagnostics. Drawing on preliminary fieldwork in Delhi and Hyderabad along with a review of policy documents, I trace some of the actors, institutions, and strategies employed to make genetic diagnosis work in Indian labs. As care and research overlap in contemporary biotechnology, what kinds of motivations are key in administering genetic testing and screening of the Indian population? What kinds of discursive formations sustain the proliferation of genetic diagnostic technologies in India? More generally, how are technologies that have a universal purchase – in this case, DNA sequencing for precision diagnosis and treatment – brokered according to the contingencies of market logics, policy visions, and disease biologies?

The Encoded Universal Psyche: Algorithms of Care and its Boundaries *Claudia Lang, Institute of Anthropology - University of Leipzig*

Accelerated by the pandemic, the search for technical fixes to the

mental health and wellbeing crisis through the use of artificial intelligence has enticed engineers and psychologists to experiment with technological innovations. This paper focuses on the making and use of Wysa, a digital couch or virtual psychotherapist, developed in India. By feeding the chatbot's algorithms with an eclectic mix of evidence-based therapies, Wysa's designers and programmers engage the science of psychology to produce a streamlined understanding of wellbeing. In the process they literally encode the universal psyche in these technologies, thus rendering it portable. However, the universality of this understanding of mental health does not go uncontested. Based on fieldwork with the app's developers and users, and with the chatbot itself, I investigate how psychological and psychotherapeutic universalisms in digital mental health are engaged, encoded, and contested. Which assumptions about suffering, needs and care are programmed into the chatbot's algorithms? How does the situated knowledge of developers impact their engagement with and choice of psychotherapeutic schools and the affective labor of the bot? Which people and forms of suffering are excluded? How does the app shape the way people care for their mental wellbeing as they engage with Wysa's style of questioning, responding, and "caring"? How do users contest the app's universality and the rendering digital of mental health care more generally? In this discussion I draw on the notion of "neutral accent" (Aneesh 2015) to probe how digital mental health enacts both its universality and its boundaries.

(Re)Creating Psychology in Africa: Colonial Legacies, Current Debates, Future Visions *Julia Vorhölder, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology*

Inspired by broader calls for decolonizing knowledge in African universities, psychologists in Africa have recently started debating the necessity and feasibility of creating a distinctly African psychology as a new academic discipline and field of practice. Some view this idea – either skeptically or enthusiastically – as a primarily political move; others are more concerned with the philosophical question regarding the possibilities, and the boundaries, of universality within sciences. While critics warn of the risks of exoticizing and further marginalizing "African" psychology from what they see as a universal discipline, proponents argue that mainstream "Western psychology" has so far been harmful, or at best irrelevant, for Africans. My paper engages with these recent debates, drawing on my fieldwork among psychologists and psychotherapists in Uganda, where psychology has only very recently started to gain popularity. Although my practitioner-interlocutors were enthusiastic about what psychology, a new and largely foreign discipline, could offer both themselves and their students and clients, they were constantly faced with the challenge of adapting the theories, concepts, and methodologies they had learned from western textbooks to fit Ugandan realities. It was through their ongoing creative practices of enacting psychology that a distinctively Ugandan, though not yet consolidated, form of psychology was gradually emerging. Using ethnographic examples and drawing on the work of Annemarie Mol, my paper proposes the idea of a "psychology multiple" – a partially universal, partially coherent, and partially coordinated discipline which is constantly being (re)created through diverse localized practices and situated knowledges.

Experimenting Across the Boundaries of Model Ecosystems in European "Rewilding" Nature Reserves *Desirée Kumpf, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology*

In this presentation, I discuss how contestations of model ecosystems create participatory politics in the more-than-human context of rewilding conservation. Based on preliminary results from a multispecies study of nature reserves in Italy, Poland, and Germany, I explore how different actors negotiate the implementation of model ecosystems. I examine such collaborative experimentation as a way in which "universal" assumptions about ecological relations are utilized and adjusted

in dynamically changing eco-social contexts. Rewilding conservation approaches are particularly inspired by the ecosystem model of trophic cascades, which stresses the importance of large mammals for the food chain. Biologists and policy makers work to (re-)introduce predators and herbivore herds, or build wildlife corridors in sparsely populated regions. But they also acknowledge that model ecosystems are abstract representations suited for hypothesizing and not stable reference points. "In the wild," ecological relations are always modified by local residents as well as the modeled animals themselves. Thus, the contestation of model ecosystems becomes the basis for new more-than-human socialities (i.e. "Bear Smart" communities), which create both conflicts and potentials. Examining the "boundary work" involved in regenerating biodiversity in contemporary Europe, I argue that, instead of delivering a "universal" template, ecosystem models are used as a starting point for collaborative experimentation. I pay particular attention to both the exclusions or inequalities thus created, and the potential for new socialities.

Session Organizers:

Hanna Nieber, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology
Hynek Bečka, Institute of Anthropology - University of Leipzig

Chair:

Michiel Baas, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology

Discussant:

Hanna Werner, Max-Weber-Kolleg, University of Erfurt

295. Genealogies of the Human in AI Systems I.

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

From rational actors to addicted users, Eurocentric theories of mind and society inform the design of AI/ML systems, both explicitly and through uninterrogated universalising norms and assumptions. Scholarly work has examined the societal impacts of AI systems, but less has been done to examine the assumptions of the social that inform such systems. This panel explores a genealogy of the human in the machine, examining AI systems as a palimpsest of conceptions of mind and society inherited from the fields that feed into AI research including cognitive science, behavioural psychology, economics, and philosophy. We seek to tease apart the models and paradigms of the human that are translated into code, used to act on, navigate, categorise and govern the world. Hubert Dreyfus famously drew on phenomenology to challenge the rationalist assumptions of human intelligence underlying AI research. "Facts and rules"-based theories of intelligence have given way to a neural network paradigm, responding in part to Dreyfus' challenge. Yet the question of what notions of the human are entangled in AI systems remains—calling us to examine not only conceptions of human intelligence—but also human bodies and human social structures. We invite papers examining how paradigms of mind and society are explicitly encoded, invisibly inscribed, and entirely omitted from AI/ML design and exploring the consequences of these encodings and erasures. We are particularly interested in work exploring AI systems as situated in racial capitalism and colonialism and the racialised and gendered dimension of the human as encoded in AI systems.

Participants:

AI and the Unsullied Self *W.E. King, University of Washington;*
Os Keyes, University of Washington

Artificial intelligence (AI) depends implicitly and explicitly on particular views of knowledge, reason, the human mind and notions of personal identity/the self. From attempts to build the prophesied "strong AI" systems to more mundane expert systems and machine learning (ML) technologies, there are countless examples of how models of intelligence and reason relied upon are implicitly white, western, and masculine (see Alison Adam, *Artificial Knowing: Gender and the Thinking Machine* (1998), Lorraine Code (1991), *What Can She Know?: Feminist Theory and the Construction of Knowledge*, David F. Noble (1999), *The Religion of Technology: The Divinity of Man and the Spirit of Invention*). These works attend to genealogies of reason,

however, in this presentation we turn to genealogies of the self: the ways in which algorithmic systems designed to respond to human identity rely on a very particular conception of selfhood. White, western, and masculine models of human reasoning and the self construct individuals as having continuous access to memory/historical information as well as the capacity to make decisions based on that access. The construction of a person's "data doppelgänger" interacts with predictive systems that reason from historical information, maximize information availability, and consider all data as potentially relevant. Drawing on examples from facial recognition, credit reporting, and dating platforms, we highlight how Enlightenment notions of the self - as inevitably, historically rooted, as already-developed, and as dependent on an entirely accessible form of the past - constrains the conditions of possibility for those without untrammelled access to a continuous past.

“Artificial Ignorance: A Retronymic Countergeneology of AI”
Katherine Behar, Baruch College, City University of New York

The term “artificial ignorance” theorizes the unprecedented capacities of digital technologies together with the fuzzy analog irregularities that persist—and even proliferate—in them. This retronymic approach to understanding AI technologies inverts expectations that “intelligence” and knowledge production would be core functions of digital computational practices. As an analytic device, artificial ignorance enables us to ask such questions as: of what to remain willfully ignorant? How do AI-enabled interactions script humans into ignorance? How do AI technologies overlap with and differ from the autonomic filtering capacities of human cognition? Using artificial ignorance, we can approach these questions in their ethical dimensions, exploring specifically how AI-enabled systems are perhaps most human-like in implementation. That is, when—like us—they fail to live up to intelligence’s ideals, and behave ignorantly. Guided by the premise that ignorance in AI is a feature rather than a bug, I chart a path between feminist epistemologies in agnotology [Tuana and Sullivan, 2006; Proctor and Schiebinger, 2008] and critical media studies [Broussard 2019; Noble 2018; Eubanks, 2019; Browne, 2015; Benjamin, 2019; O’Neil, 2017; Angwin, et al., 2017; others], and by drawing on Katherine Hayle’s notion of the “cognitive nonconscious” [Hayles, 2017] and Wendy Chun’s notion of “discriminating data” [Chun, forthcoming] develop a notion I call “ignorant ignoring.” Through this lens, I address how various concrete technologies at work in AI—in particular, algorithmic decision-making in classification, and adversarial networks in machine learning—produce limitations in knowledge, culture, politics, and social relations as they are constructed informatically.

Containing Superintelligence: Governing Global Change through AI Safety
Apolline Taillandier, The University of Cambridge

This presentation proposes a contextual history of “artificial intelligence (AI) safety” as transnational public discourse and technoscientific practice from the early 2010s onwards. AI safety intersects AI and machine learning research, policy expertise and technological forecasting, with the aim to prepare for risks of future AI systems with “high-level” or “superintelligent capabilities,” by ensuring continuous “alignment” between AI goals and human interests. Drawing on technical AI safety literature, popular science essays and interviews with AI safety researchers, I examine how AI risk and mitigation strategies are defined in specific sites of corporate and academic research in the United States and the United Kingdom. I locate AI safety in the context of the history of AI as contested field and object, but also of transhumanist conceptions of long-term future, manageable uncertainty, and existential risk. AI safety expertise involves specific machine learning methods, behavioral models of rationality, universal “non-anthropomorphic” measures of intelligence, and scenarios and metrics of AI progress. I discuss

how AI safety experts redefine AI practice, human interests and global sustainability, especially the realist lens through which they understand systemic change as produced by cooperation and competition dynamics. A set of strategies for taming technological risks, social disruption and political unrest, AI safety enacts global imaginaries of scientific stewardship and market governance while justifying ongoing practices of “behavioral surplus” extraction. Finally, I examine how AI safety visions of future world order challenge or reinforce global economic, social and racial hierarchies.

Magic, Rationality and the Making of AI Technologies
Alexandrine Royer, University of Cambridge

The entrenched legacy of the Enlightenment in Eurocentric theories of mind has allowed science to stand as the beacon of human empiricism and rational thought. Research in artificial intelligence has benefitted from this confidence that all scientific outputs are derived from the careful application of universal human reasoning. Diana Forsythe’s (1993) early study of AI practitioners effectively demonstrated how knowledge within this scientific community is situated and localized rather than representative of a universal common sense. Building on Forsythe, Kathleen Richardson (2016) introduced the concept of ‘technological animism’ in the creation and production of humanoid robots, whereby the experimental settings of robotic laboratories allow myth, fiction and scientific exploration to converge. While scholars have long pointed to human’s animistic tendencies in interactions with animate and inanimate objects, few have reflected on the instincts to humanize non-human intelligence from the early stages of conceptualization and design. In this paper, I draw on interviews with roboticists, computer scientists, and cognitive scientists on the role of imagination, reason, enchantment, and belief in creating artificial intelligent systems, where the stated purpose of such systems is to mimic, and go beyond, human cognitive abilities. I argue for a deeper consideration of how belief, faith and scientific reason interplay in the work of AI designers and within their understandings of the human mind. Gut feelings, and technological fantasies popularized through mass media, often inform AI design, allowing for conscious or subconscious racialized and gendered conceptions of the human to creep into these systems.

Optimization machines: the peculiar reversal of rationality
Udo Pesch, Delft University of Technology

Modern philosophers have reconstructed the human mind as an ‘optimization machine’, it was turned into a rational instrument that allowed mankind, or more specifically a specific type of men, to make optimal decisions. Thinking was considered to be taking place within the individual brain, in a linear way, converting input into output and allowing for the most optimal actions and decisions by taken a wide range of alternative options into consideration. In this, emotions and other physical distractions have been considered as disturbances, an assumption that could conveniently be used to exclude women and ‘non-civilized’ people as rational beings. Empirical studies have showed that this reconstruction has been incorrect, but instead of acknowledging this recognizing empirical and moral failures, the dominant vision is that rationality is the ideal of cognition, while the human cognition is seen as a deviation from the norm. Digital computing and especially artificial intelligence can be seen as the technical fulfilment of this ideal, effectuating the incorrect assumptions about how the mind works. An abundance of resources is committed to turn the flawed ideal of rationality into a reality. As such rationality, originally considered to be a defining feature of mankind, is transferred to machines that force us to make optimized decisions. In my paper I will describe the reconstruction of the mind in philosophy, the way this reconstruction motivated the development of artificial intelligence and I will discuss the institutional repercussions of the subsequent devaluation of the human mind.

Session Organizer:

Alexa Hagerty, University of Cambridge

296. Same Same but Different: Race and Racializations across National, Disciplinary and Temporal Contexts - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

In human diversity research, race is a moving target. It is rarely clearly defined, and takes on different meanings and labels in different contexts, and often reveals itself as racialized connotations of other terms. From an international perspective, it is apparent that while race is used in political and scientific contexts in the USA or Brazil, for example, in continental Europe, by contrast, today it is commonly considered a taboo. This difference is partly rooted in divergent conceptual meanings in different languages, and various political as well as scientific strategies for dealing with the historical burden of the concept. However, even in countries that are largely imagined as post-racial, race remains as an “absent presence” (M’charek/Schramm/Skinner 2014) within other terms in use such as “ethnicity”, “population”, “migrant background”, “biogeographical ancestry”, “metapopulation” etc. In this panel we welcome contributions inquiring into the national, disciplinary and/or temporal specifics of human difference categorizations – with a focus on, but not limited to, the life sciences. We are particularly interested in the shaping of processes of categorization and in the continuity and discontinuity of concepts of group classification across/in different contexts and specific situations. Possible topics include: * entanglements between race and “ethnicity”, “caste”, “populations” etc. * context-specific and language-related differences and similarities between racialized concepts, wordings, meanings, and their historical dis/continuities * travelling concepts, translations, euphemisms, modernizations, and equivocations * processes of racialization in various scientific disciplines * race after race, post-racial racializations, racializations in antiracism * effects of notions like “colourblindness”, “race-consciousness”, “race realism”, “social constructivism” * different bureaucratic-administrative regulations of race, e.g. in the law, in affirmative action, surveys, censuses etc. * attempts to grasp diversity/variation in a non-racialized manner

Participants:

Old Bones in New Databases: the Case of ForDisc *Iris Clever*,
University of Chicago; Lisette Jong, *Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research*, *University of Amsterdam*

The use of racial categorization practices in the discipline of forensic anthropology is a recurring matter of debate. Anthropologists arguing for the usefulness of ancestry estimation rely on a perceived correspondence between biological traits and social race categories, while critical voices in anthropology and STS stress the problematic reproduction of typological and biological understandings of race through these practices. In this paper we take a closer look at ForDisc, software that automates the estimation of ancestry by comparing measurements of an unknown skeleton to reference samples from several skeletal collections. We trace the data journey of one of these collections, the “E series”, to Karl Pearson’s Biometric Laboratory in early 20th century London where this collection of 1800 Egyptian skulls was central to the development of Pearson’s novel statistical study of race. In the 1960s, American physical anthropologist William Howells remeasured the “E-series” wishing to transform older typological notions of race by extending Pearson’s statistical analysis of cranial variation. Howells’s cranial database, including the Egyptian data, today lives on in ForDisc as developed by Jantz and Ousley (2005) to enhance the ‘objectivity’ of ancestry estimation methods. We employ the case of ForDisc and the “E series” to address how historical collection methods and notions of race stick to data practices and are accordingly “folded” (M’charek 2014) into modern technologies like ForDisc. We argue that these historical entanglements prevent forensic anthropology from moving beyond problematic notions of race and raise critical questions about the reuse of old data in new technologies.

Minjok in flux: Group classification and racialization in South Korean genomics and beyond *Jaehwan Hyun*, *Pusan National University*

This paper examines South Korean genomicists’ categorizing work using a local grouping category, minjok, and its racialization of the Korean population and Asian minorities. In South Korea, minjok, originally derived from the German ethnonational notion of Volk in the late 19th century, has been used as an inclusive, flexible concept embracing the ideas of race, ethnicity, tribe, and nation in English usage. Korean genomicists studying the genetic history and developing ancestry informative markers (AIMs) of their population employ it in their scientific activities. They also interpret foreign genomic research adopting a variety of grouping categories in the minjok framework. The conceptual plasticity of minjok allows Korean researchers to avoid the debate over race in genomics while using the term in a de facto racial sense. The impact of their racialization work is not limited to the domestic genomicist community but extends to other social worlds – particularly immigration governance and public health sectors – and the global biomedical community. This paper traces the categorical work in genomic research and the circulation of minjok usage beyond the Korean genomicist circle. Doing so will illuminate how the scientists play a role in inscribing race in migration management and biomedicine despite their self-image as “post-racial” scientists in a “non-racial” country.

Making race: the plantation world beyond abolition *Cristiana Bastos*, *University of Lisbon; Marta Macedo*, *Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon*

In this paper we will discuss the processes of racialization of plantation labor in post abolition societies. We will address the morphing of plantation nomenclatures of labor, hierarchy and race into different nomenclatures of ethnicity, ancestry or nationality, with an emphasis on indentured labor migrations and forced displacements. We will refer to examples from Guyana, Mauritius, Fiji, Hawaii and São Tomé – expanding on this as a case-study. As a small equatorial island in the Gulf of Guinea with an history shaped by a succession of monocrops and exploitative labor regimes, São Tomé provides a rich case to explore the dynamics of race-making, to analyse how the practices and technologies involved in cultivating and processing sugarcanes, coffee and cocoa beans and oil palms fruits produced racialized working bodies, and how those practices were codified into the managerial knowledge at the root of imperial domination. We will further discuss the derivative uses of racialist knowledge in post abolition plantations in the continuum between forced and free labor.

Nomadic Fields: The erasure of violence in the Aché fieldwork of Pierre Clastres and Carleton Gajdusek *Sebastián Gil-Riaño*, *University of Pennsylvania*

How has field science effaced the violence endured by indigenous groups who refuse contact? My paper examines the work of two field scientists – Pierre Clastres and Carleton Gajdusek – who produced scientific studies about the Aché (a forest-dwelling and traditionally nomadic group in Paraguay) in the 1960s. After the Aché were forced to settle on a Paraguayan ranch, Clastres and Gajdusek coincided in the “field” and conducted studies with contrasting styles. Clastres, a student of Claude Lévi-Strauss, lived among the Aché with his wife Helen Clastres for several months. He then wrote an elegiac ethnography, *Chronique des Indiens Guayaki* (1972), that described the Aché as destined to disappear due to western civilization’s inevitable expansion. After his Aché fieldwork, Clastres made important contributions in political anthropology and became famous for his conception of primitive society as “society against the State.” Gajdusek, by contrast, spent one week on the Aché ranch with the Clastres’ acting as his guides. Gajdusek travelled to Paraguay to collect blood samples from

indigenous groups as part of a WHO project concerned with the population genetics of “primitive groups”. Though his aim was to “bleed” as many as possible, Gajdusek also kept a journal filled with extensive ethnographic observations where he marveled at the Ache’s “astounding whiteness” and described the rampant spread of a “grippe-like disease”. By situating these two accounts in the context of extractivism and internal colonization, my paper considers how scientific regimes of race and human diversity have effaced the colonial violence endured by indigenous groups.

Session Organizers:

Jenny Reardon, UC Santa Cruz

Mihai Surdu, Research Centre on

Antigypsyism/Forschungsstelle Antiziganismus

Andrea zur Nieden, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Nils Ellebrecht, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Chairs:

Thiago Pinto Barbosa, Universität Bayreuth

Tino Pluemecke, Institute for Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Discussant:

Veronika Lipphardt, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, University College Freiburg

297. Vectors – I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Anything that has both direction and magnitude can be described as a vector. Take a billiard ball. Standing still, it is just a ball. But set in motion, it has new capacities and potentials: it can hit another ball on the table; it can rearrange the board. Or take a mosquito. Alone, it is an insect—ostensibly an isolated being. But once it has been infected with a pathogen, it can spread disease, cause death, change worlds. Toxics, dust storms, super-spreaders: all of these are vectors, too. What can we learn by taking up vectors as objects of analysis? That is, what can we learn by looking at our research objects in their vector forms? We invite contributions from scholars working on a range of objects (medical, environmental, mathematical, political, or otherwise) who are interested in exploring those objects in motion. How do they become relational pathways—entities that spread, link up, cross scales, and expand from points of origin? Can vectors be both problems and blueprints for solving them? Can they be both objects and methods? Does rethinking the object-as-vector invite us to make connections that are otherwise obscure? And what about the researcher-as-vector? Covid-19 throws old ethical quandaries about fieldwork into harrowing relief, pressing questions like: what do “good relations” look like when there is not even a pretense of separation or neutrality? When the scholar-body poses an explicit risk, and is itself at risk, how should that change the ways we go about our work?

Participants:

Brazilian Vectors: Mosquitoes, Microbes, and the Geopolitics of Knowledge Production *Luisa Reis Castro, University of Southern California*

A bite from the *Aedes aegypti* mosquito can be a harmful, even deadly encounter—if the insect is infected with the Zika, dengue, chikungunya or yellow fever viruses. Because of this vectorial capacity, the insect has been framed as a conveyor of death and targeted as a winged enemy to be destroyed. In Brazil, for more than one hundred years, public health campaigns have attempted to eliminate the *Aedes aegypti* by urging humans to destroy breeding spots and employing insecticides. New strategies, however, strive to biologically modify these mosquitoes in order to deploy them in controlling the very viruses the insect can transmit. One of these strategies entails artificially infecting *Aedes aegypti* with bacterium *Wolbachia*, which significantly reduces viral transmission. As part of a Global Health project funded by the Gates Foundation, Brazilian researchers have been

releasing these bioengineered insects throughout the streets of Rio de Janeiro. Drawing upon ten months of fieldwork with researchers and technicians from this project, I investigate how these releases transform both the local biopolitics of infection and the international geopolitics of knowledge production. To do so, I analyze how the *Wolbachia*-project not only attempts to transform the *Aedes aegypti* from a vector of pathogenic viruses into a “vector of health,” but it also aims to transform Brazil from a country historically plagued by mosquito-borne diseases into one that offers solutions on how to tackle them, worldwide. These vectorial inversions are, therefore, simultaneously taking place at multiple scales: mosquito bodies, national public health campaigns, and global discussions on the future of diseases.

Spreading the News: Media as a Vector for Pandemic Knowledge *Jorge Benavides-Rawson, George Washington University*

In 2015 it was difficult to read or watch the news without being confronted with the image of a child born with microcephaly due to the Zika Virus. During the Ebola outbreaks of 2013 and 2018 we had images of burials and personal protective equipment. COVID-19 has produced its share of imagery: masks, needles, empty cities, virtual rituals. Due to pandemic restrictions, more than ever before, citizens consume almost all information about their town, country, and the world through mediated spaces: newspapers, news channels and websites, social media platforms, and peer-to-peer digital messaging. For more than a year, we have watched how journalists question and pressure government officials on live TV, doctors and scientists reach celebrity status, and state governments argue for their interpretation of the pandemic and beg their constituents to follow official advice. At the same time, critiques of face masks as oppression, anti vaccination messages, and conspiracy theories about the pandemic made their way into our social media, direct messages, and even some cable news. In this paper I use vectors as idiom and metaphor to analyze how media outlets select, shape, and disseminate health science knowledge. Outside of recent work on “Infodemics,” health-related media has been generally overlooked as an object of analysis in STS. Tracing information and disinformation as vector-borne knowledge can provide novel insights into the social production of pandemic knowledge.

Sickness, Sweating, Signs: Transitive Toxics after the BP Spill *Danielle Good*

In a poem titled *Sweat*, a collaborator shared the ins and outs of toxic waters and bodies he cannot avoid in South Alabama with me. “I swim in the humidity of the Coast // As if I were in the Gulf of Mexico itself // As if I would do that again // I come out drenched either way // Toxins in or out.” This paper takes skin as a vector of toxicity and healing after the BP Deepwater Horizon disaster, following many encounters with similar attention to sweat, pores, and rashes in discussions of oil and dispersant exposure. I term the way spill-related illness traveled through sweat, skin, and touch transitive toxicity to show the relationships and equivalencies that informed embodied logics of exposure. Transitivity informed how workers and coastal residents knew they were sick and what they did to treat their illnesses. This work also questions the legal class-action settlement addressing health issues after BP, which assigned little systemic and financial importance to chronic conditions like rashes. Despite this, rashes were some of the most remarked upon, persistent health problems from the spill. This confounding disjuncture in the Medical Settlement Agreement’s valuation of illnesses encouraged creative modes of recognition and healing strategies. Detoxification through sweat clinics, supplements from herbalists, and homeopathy, each inverting exposure to pollutants into therapeutics through a transitive logic of “like treats like,” became more viable treatments for exposure than financial settlement.

Vectors for a cashless world *maríel Garcia Garcia Llorens, UC*

Davis Anthropology

Until the Covid-19 pandemic started, paper money and coins were the preferred and most prevalent means of exchange for most Peruvians, who tend to mistrust the surveillance of governments and banks, both of which are often involved in corruption scandals. With Covid-19, along with martial law and never-ending nationwide lockdowns, cash was suddenly seen as a potential vector of virus transmission, and that outweighs the risk of being trackable by banks and the state. Over the five years that I have been studying the prototyping and deployment of Peru's Billetera Movil (Bim) nothing has helped spread its use like the coronavirus. Bim was the world's first mobile money platform developed and marketed as a partnership of banks collaborating with the state's financial inclusion goal. Mobile money platforms are obviously a vector for money, facilitating new kinds of cashless transactions. Bim also promised to be a vector for "financialization of development," pulling "the unbanked" into a formal banking sector. But, as of 2019, it hardly had any users, even as it continued to grow and change through shifting collaborations among banks, governments, telecom corporations, and international NGOs, all pursuing (and prototyping) the ideology of a cashless society with total inclusion. In 2020, though, the use of Bim grows rapidly. This paper explores how the materiality of the virus interrupts Bim's ideological promises and therefore reforms Bim's materiality too, allowing it to become a vector for financial corporations penetrating the "informal" everyday economies-- and the entire lives- of the "unbanked" poor.

The Meter, the App, and the Origin: Displacement as a Spatial Logic of Mobility and the Speculative Enclosure of Movement *William F Stafford Jr, University of Toronto Mississauga*

While undertaking fieldwork on autorickshaws in Delhi during the early emergence of app-based transit platforms, a curious feature of booking a trip through an app was that one could not have the trip end where it began. While it is possible to move from and return to the origin, this curious stipulation speaks to a more general principle through which apps transactionalize the space of mobility. In this paper, I explore the vector form of the 'origin of the journey' within spaces of transit to describe how journeys as transactional units are constructed by on-demand transport platforms. I draw specifically on the difference between the measurement of distance as the measure of a magnitude and the measurement of displacement as a measure of the separation between an origin and a destination that takes into account the direction of movements between these two points. Using displacement as an interpretive lens, I show how a prohibition against the identity of origins and destinations imparts a unique seriality to journeys, reversing the familiar temporal order between origin and destination in order to transform the space of the city itself from a distribution of places into a dynamic field of vectors. Understanding this transformation is key to understanding how movement is paradoxically enclosed as a form of speculative accumulation, and how limits imposed on the fungibility of place facilitate this aim.

Session Organizer:

Jorge Benavides-Rawson, George Washington University

Chair:

Chloe Ahmann, Cornell University

Discussant:

Andrew Lakoff, University of Southern California

298. Computers and Assetization: Organizational and Historical Approaches

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

The panel interrogates the bi-directional relationship between digital computing technologies on the one hand, and developments and dynamics

in capitalist political economy on the other. Specifically, papers in this session examine the relationship between computing technologies and the process of assetization by which various types of material artifacts or practices are turned into assets. Inspired by the work of Katharina Pistor (*Code of Capital*, 2019) as well as Kean Birch and Fabien Muniesa's recent volume (*Assetization and Technoscientific Capitalism*, 2020), we invite new readings of emerging organizational networks that shift the lens from seemingly bounded 'tech giants' to an ecosystem of networked actors that together assetize data, computing power, and software. We explore how differences in computing technologies, from the mainframe to time-sharing, to the cloud, enable and inform new ways of conceiving of capital assets; and reciprocally, how business practices, and economic models of capital assets shape computer technologies, IT organizations, and even computer science itself. We focus on how a new infrastructural terrain reconfigures industrial and commercial practices -- from altering the global market for business applications and enterprise products to fuelling new partnerships between industry and enterprise platforms and social media platforms. Together, the four papers offer historical, empirical, and sociological perspectives on the different forms computing capital has taken and the specific practices of assetization, commodification, and monetization these forms rest upon.

Participants:

Of Products and Platforms: New organizational forms and market dynamics in India's computing industry *Devika Narayan*

This paper contributes to emerging literature on platforms economies and new digital infrastructures. Large-scale data centers represent an important element of platform economies and scholars of STS have closely examined this. Less clear is the link between this configuration of hardware and the new dynamics of software development. The fact is, data centers aggregate computing capacity by centralizing hardware resources and in doing so fuel a globally distributed and organizationally decentralized ecosystem of startups. Platform studies, in examining a new infrastructural regime, is beginning to engage ecosystem-level dynamics, probing the relationship between centralized, core layers (data centers, platforms) and more varied and flexible outer layers (software applications). This paper advances these discussions by illuminating 1) new organizational and market dynamics 2) new global and transnational networks and 3) the importance of engaging business-to-business relations. The analysis presented is based on extensive qualitative fieldwork in India's software industry. Using over 100 interviews, this paper tracks the rise of a new cluster of business-facing startups in India that sell business applications and software products to firms in the west. It emphasizes how platformization fuels hyper-competition between entrepreneurs, gives birth to new organizational forms, and reconfigures the geography of software production.

Computers, Assetization, and Productivity in the West German Financial Industry *Corinna Schlombs, Rochester Institute of Technology*

This paper investigates how mainframe computers turned from wartime instruments of national security into corporate assets that were expected to create revenue. Studying the post-WWII West German financial industry in the two post-WWII decades, the paper looks at networks of corporate executives, engineers, consultants, and business organizations comparing computers to alternative assets, such as manual labor. Company size, labor costs, and availability of financial resources were among the factors shaping corporate reasoning about computing assets. While rationalization justified the acquisition of computing assets in some cases, computerization was delayed in others. At the same time, computers were part of a regime of US-style productivity technologies intended to reshape the West German capitalist political economy after the US model. Higher productivity, that is higher output per worker, increased corporate revenue streams; it went along with changes in company size and

ownership structures. Americans suggested that revenue streams be shared by owners, workers and consumers in a dynamically growing economy, but established social and labor relations in West Germany helped uphold the idea that finite resources needed to be distributed between capital and labor. The paper argues that local economic and corporate factors shaped assetization, and that assetization in turn shaped those factors. Focusing on West Germany, it contributes a historical and internationally comparative perspective based on sources from corporate and national archives. It critically interrogates generalizing assumptions about computers and assetization, suggesting these are not universal but shaped by local economic and social conditions.

Assetization and platformization: the significance of partnerships in social media *Anne Helmond, University of Amsterdam; Fernando van der Vlist, Utrecht University and University of Siegen*

This paper considers the significance of partnerships in the integrated platform ecosystem of social media. More specifically, it explores how partners mediate and shape platform power through infrastructure development. We argue how partners play a key role in the technological and organisational process of platformization, driving the technological expansion and economic growth of digital platforms into other markets, industries, and societal domains. Partners include leading audience intermediaries that shape the creation, buying, modelling, and targeting of data assets and build the business-to-business relationships that integrate social media with the digital advertising market. We present an empirical study of the partnerships of leading social media to situate them in the audience economy and identify aspects of platform power. The paper highlights the strategic importance of partnerships in the processes of assetization and platformization. Ultimately, our contribution situates platforms, their data assets, and their sources of power within an integrated platform ecosystem.

Capital as a matter of computation: industrial operations and computer science in the United States, 1947-1967 *Devin Kennedy, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

During the 1950s and 1960s, manufacturing firms were responsible for the largest share of computer acquisitions and leases in the United States. More than simply sites of early adoption, however, factories and industrial operations became laboratories and model problems for the development of new ideas in computer science. This paper documents how mathematical challenges associated with managing fixed capital—including scheduling, inventory management, and planning industrial equipment—became central computational problems in the emerging fields of optimization research, database management, and computer simulation. Siting these intellectual developments within corporate efforts to deskill industrial labor and geographically reorganize factory production in an assault on postwar union power, this paper describes early and specific patterns of influence between capitalism and computational ideas in the Cold War. It concludes by describing three products of the fusion of capital and digital computing in this period: the development of national time-sharing infrastructure for large manufacturing firms, the assetization of computer time, and finally, new methods for optimizing financial risk through computer-based portfolio management techniques.

Session Organizers:

Devin Kennedy, University of Wisconsin-Madison
Devika Narayan

299. Changing Terrains of Carbon and Climate

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

While hurricanes, fires, floods, and droughts threaten much of the planet, the oil, gas, and coal industries are changing so rapidly that interpretation

struggles to keep pace. Changes to extractive industries are in some cases linked to the climate crisis, but are also driven by global market perturbations, the Covid-19 pandemic, and other forces. In some interpretations, pressures on fossil fuel companies are opening up space for alternative technologies and lower-carbon imaginaries. From other perspectives, rapacious companies are finding ways to position themselves favorably in these rough waters, heeding the adage of "never let a good crisis go to waste." In this paper session, we intend to address several questions about these processes of change. How are fossil fuel companies adapting to climate change, and even sponsoring climate adaptation initiatives? What are the dynamics of climate justice activism at the sites of fossil fuel production? How are the technosocial relations of fossil fuel extraction changing at different sites along the production chain in response to climate change and related crises? What new forms of expertise are authorized to deal with these industries? How do both experts and laypeople create knowledge that can help them understand and navigate the intersecting changes to the climate and the industries upon which they depend? How can crisis in the oil and gas industry be capitalized upon, not by industry actors but by those seeking more just and sustainable energy relations?

Participants:

Conflicted Transitions: Actors, Tactics, and Outcomes of Energy Infrastructure Opposition and Community Mobilization in Carbon-intensive Regions *Roberto Cantoni, University of Sussex*

Given the growing frequency, severity, and salience of social mobilization and community action on energy and climate issues, in this study we systematically explore the actors, tactics, and outcomes of recent opposition to low-carbon transitions across seven geographic carbon intensive regions in Asia, Europe, and North America. Based on an original dataset of 130 case studies spanning the past decade, we investigate how often protests occur, and against which forms of energy infrastructure, including low-carbon options such as renewable energy and nuclear power. We examine the actors and coalitions involved in such events, their tactics (such as litigation or protest), and their outcomes (such as remuneration, policy change, concessions, or labor protections). We show how the configurations of actors, tactics, and outcomes can be explained by differences in national institutions and thus show the value of both a sociotechnical and comparative perspective for understanding conflicts over energy transitions.

Envisioning "The Just Transition:" The Sociotechnical Imaginaries of Energy Workers *Diane Sicotte, Drexel University; Kelly Joyce, Drexel University; Arielle Hesse, Drexel University*

Recently, the threat of climate change and the promise of the expansion of "green jobs" has refocused attention on the prospect of transitioning away from the use of fossil fuels in the United States. The "just transition" has been a topic of concern for environmentalists, but workers potentially displaced from their jobs and organized labor in the trades and energy sector more generally are mostly viewed as obstacles to progress or passive recipients of clean energy policies. In this study, part of a larger project on labor and energy, we focus on in-depth interviews with 101 labor union members and leaders in New Jersey, New York and Pennsylvania. We compare and contrast energy workers with non-energy workers' sociotechnical imaginaries of energy futures. When asked what energy system they would like to see in the future, workers envisioned heterogeneous and sometimes competing visions of the ideal energy future. The ways workers make sense of the anticipated transition away from fossil fuel energy sources allow us to examine the conflict between the need for environmental sustainability and the need for livelihood, and the political economy of the "just transition." Some of these imagined energy futures embody resistance to energy transitions, while others embody resistance to imagined neoliberal fossil fuel energy projects. All are political projects

that are both functional and instrumental, embodying labor's push for centrality in the creation and governance of energy transitions.

Factualities of carbon data and imaginaries of oil in Stavanger, Norway *Anne-Sofie Lautrup Sørensen, IT University of Copenhagen*

From climate models to carbon budgets and carbon footprints, carbon data figures increasingly as a material in social and political life. This paper explores the role of carbon data in local understandings of Norwegian oil and gas production and carbon data's position in negotiations over low-carbon futures. The paper draws on ethnographic fieldwork in the Norwegian oil-capital Stavanger among young climate activists and people working in the oil and gas sector. Stavanger is an especially interesting case: inhabitants are acutely aware of the destructive consequences of the oil and gas industry for the global climate, while oil and gas make up the foundation of the local labor market and the finances of the national welfare state. Furthermore, in the relatively small city of Stavanger, activists and industry people often share social ties of friendship or family. The paper shows how carbon data is emically constructed as a fact that can be mobilized in a fact- and data-centric debate over the future of the oil industry. In conversation with scholarship on sociotechnical imaginaries (Jasanoff and Kim 2015; McNeil et al. 2017) the paper argues that differing imaginaries of oil play into how youth and industry people respectively understand, interpret and use carbon data as fact. Through an engagement with Michelle Murphy's (2006) work on regimes of perceptibility the paper puts these findings in conversation with questions about the different types of knowledge that are at stake when living with the local multiplicity of the climate crisis in an oil city.

Grassroots Coalitions and Energy Justice in North America: Strategy, Knowledge, and Pipeline Opposition *David J Hess, Vanderbilt; Kaelee Belletto, Vanderbilt University, Sociology Department*

The study continues to develop a project that develops a better understanding of how conditions, coalition composition, frames, and tactics contribute to outcomes for energy infrastructure opposition movements. This study focuses on coalitions that include indigenous peoples (Canadian First Nations, Native Americans, etc.) in campaigns to stop pipelines that occurred in the U.S. and Canada between 2010 and 2020. Of particular interest from an STS perspective is the role of different types of knowledge claims made by diverse actors, including those of indigenous peoples, developer companies, government officials, environmentalists, climate activists, non-indigenous land owners, and scientists. We examine the role of diverse knowledge claims in decision-making venues (e.g., litigation and decisions by policymakers and companies) that affect outcomes of route changes, remediation, and the decision to build. More than just a study of patterns of expertise and undone science, the project also aims to identify successful and unsuccessful strategies.

Inert and Uneven Geologies – Carbon Dioxide Removal and Geological CO₂ Storage in the Anthropocene *Inge-Merete Hougaard, Lund University*

With carbon dioxide removal (CDR) increasingly envisioned as crucial for limiting climate change (Minx et al. 2018), geological CO₂ storage has become a central element in climate policy. Considering geological storage as an objectification of the underground as inert (cf. Povinelli 2016; Yusoff 2018b), this paper explores how geological CO₂ storage can be understood through the lens of the Anthropocene (Haraway et al. 2016; Lövbrand et al. 2015; Malm and Hornborg 2014; Yusoff 2018a). Based on interviews and document analysis of existing and anticipated CDR projects involving CO₂ storage, I ask how the underground is constructed and conceptualised, and how geological storage is (intended to be) operationalised. Drawing

on literature on infrastructure and the politics of knowledge and technology (Hughes 1987; Jasanoff 2004; Winner 1980), I explore what knowledges, technologies and infrastructures are imagined as needed for operating and monitoring CO₂ storage, and what actors are envisioned to control these. Acknowledging that the fossil era has benefitted a privileged minority (Malm and Hornborg 2014), I ask to what extent CDR and CO₂ storage reproduce the uneven geographies of fossil extraction and extend them to uneven geologies. I argue that by pumping CO₂ into geological deposits, where it over thousands of years will react with minerals and create new geological formations, the idea of the Anthropocene – human as a geological force that can be read in subterranean layers – becomes a self-fulfilling prophecy. Questioning whether this geological layer represents a privileged minority, I explore what political effects it has.

Making Carbon Matter? Climate Politics and the Governing of Norwegian Oil Resources *Bård Lahn, CICERO Center for International Climate Research Oslo*

A new 'existential politics' of climate change is increasingly challenging fossil fuel production. Over the last decade, a number of actors have reframed climate politics as a matter of managing carbon stocks – bringing climate targets to bear on the governing of oil and gas resources to keep fossilized carbon in the ground. In analysing how this 'carbonization' of climate politics may come to matter in the governance of oil resources, however, this paper argues that we should be careful not to take the oil itself for granted. Understanding the effects of recent attempts to connect oil and climate policymaking requires that we map in what form oil is 'made present' for political decision-making – i.e. how it is made knowable and governable through specific practices, technologies and forms of expertise. To illustrate this point, the paper provides an in-depth study of the shifting ways in which oil has been made present in the political processes of Norway during its 50 years as an oil-producing country. Drawing on the STS literature on markets and the economy, as well as approaches from political geography, the analysis identifies two contrasting ways in which oil resources are made present in Norwegian policymaking: One tied to industrial activity, and another considering oil a national 'asset'. Using the example of recent Covid-related economic relief for the oil industry, the paper argues that differentiating between the two versions of oil is key to understanding how climate politics may come to matter for the future of Norwegian oil production.

Session Organizers:

Abby Kinchy, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Jessica Lehman, Durham University

300. Towards a Typology of Relations

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

STS is approaching something of a relational turn. This is, in large part, a result of the recent rise of new materialisms and their attempts to extend accounts of social relations to nonhuman agents and material forces, to frequently generative ends. However, this work lands with a particular valence in settler colonial contexts, where Indigenous scholars have offered astute critiques of the ways that such projects come close to re-enacting non-Western ontologies of interconnection, though judiciously scrubbed of any metaphysical claims or acknowledgements of colonial legacies (Tallbear 2015, Todd 2016). Accordingly, while in both protests and paywalled papers alike, there is a call to acknowledge the material relations between human and nonhuman worlds, there is not a shared agreement of what this might mean in its particulars. If relations provide, to some degree, both a theory of everything and a site of continued incommensurate social claims, then the call for simply more relationality is likely to quickly find its limits. How then, do we proceed? This panel finds its answer through projects of categorization. It highlights papers that develop analytic vocabularies capable of distinguishing between different relational forms and effects to better assess how contrasting relational frameworks work to admit certain forms of connection while insulating themselves from others.

Grounded in both new research and scholarly engagements with the growing literature on relational methods and imperatives, the panel seeks to intervene in this quickly developing theoretical turn to seed further and more fruitful relational analytics.

Participants:

The agency of socio-technical configurations: Effects and side effects of energy innovation *Michael Ornetzeder, Austrian Academy of Sciences; Titus Udrea, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Inst. of Technology Assessment (ITA); Tanja Sinoszic, Austrian Academy of Sciences*

Technology assessment (TA) is a scientific approach grounded in practices which aim to identify unintended side-effects and risks of new technologies. Based on analyses of technology impacts it offers advice to policy-makers on how to mitigate negative implications on society and the environment. STS scholars and others have criticized TA for having a narrow, static understanding of technology and insufficient theoretical explanation of technology impacts. Technology matters in society, but what is an adequate explanation of its various effects? What actually causes these effects and how can they be managed and controlled? How does a technology, process or product innovation have a specific effect in one context, and another one in another context? This paper addresses these questions by investigating the societal implications of innovations for the energy transition in a new relational framework. In this context, it is particularly important to avoid undesirable side effects of innovations and to explore and discuss possible new effects and risks from early on. For this, we propose an approach that shifts the focus from technologies in society to technologies in use. We conceptualize technologies in use as socio-technical configurations of interrelated elements. Effects and side-effects are then the result of the specific relations between these elements. In the paper, we briefly present our approach and discuss its empirical and methodological implications using the example of alternative configurations for decentralized renewable power generation.

(Non-)Reciprocities: Relations of and Against Extraction *Jordan B. Kinder, McGill University*

This paper approaches the (non)reciprocal as a relation that both animates extraction as a settler colonial technology and offers a kind of infrastructure for moving beyond it. In doing so, the paper offers to STS a critical vocabulary for confronting the unevenly experienced risks and rewards of extraction, and for developing pathways that nurture good relations against extractive ones. Non-reciprocity is a constitutive characteristic of extractive relations and their ideological expression of extractivism. Naomi Klein's frequently cited definition of extractivism, for instance, places the nonreciprocal at the heart of its impetus. "Extractivism is a nonreciprocal, dominance-based relationship with the earth, one purely of taking," Klein (2014) writes, "It is the reduction of life into objects for the use of others, giving them no integrity or value of their own." Nonreciprocal relations, then, are those which animate extraction, an expression of what Jennifer Wenzel (2020) calls "resource logics," or ways of making sense of and acting in the world that objectifies relations in the terms that Klein lays out. Putting pressure on the nonreciprocal draws attention to the ways in which the burdens of extraction—its risks—are shouldered most heavily by the peoples and ecosystems that seek to maintain reciprocal relations. Addressing extractive infrastructures as media, this paper employs the (non-)reciprocal as an avenue through which to negotiate historical (Malm 2016), new (Yusoff 2019), and Indigenous (Todd 2017; Spice 2018) materialist approaches to infrastructure and through this negotiation it proposes a method of (non)reciprocity against extraction.

Carbon's Four Fixes: A Relational Typology for Communicating about Carbon and Thinking Elementally *Anne Pasek, Trent University*

This paper asks how carbon is relationally schematized within the work of climate change communication. Carbon's material properties as an element make this an unresolved question in contemporary climate politics. Elements are not like conventional objects of analysis; carbon exists in a large geophysical cycle, as a component of a remarkable array of substances, and so can best be defined by its relational bonds rather than properties intrinsic to itself. Accordingly, climate communication can be seen to consist of the work of constructing legible cuts across the carbon cycle, demarcating which of carbon's expansive relations are relevant and which can be disregarded. Such schema are neither definitive nor apolitical, but are nevertheless a necessary task. For carbon to be communicable, its relations and meaning must be tactically partial. This paper argues that climate politics can be productively reframed through the ways in which carbon is strategically 'fixed' into different relational schema with diverse aesthetic, affective, and economic affordances. It offers a typology of four carbon fixes – point, elliptical, transversal, and mesh structures of relation – via case studies of climate populism/denial, carbon footprinting, ecological footprinting, and carbon neutral accounting. Carbon's elemental character helps explain past challenges in climate communication and suggests future directions through which carbon's capacious relationality might serve as an asset to climate politics rather than a barrier.

Earned Trust in IoT Devices: Moving from Compliance to Relationships *Hanna Herdegen, Science and Technology in Society, Virginia Tech; Dylan Wittkower, Old Dominion University*

While conducting multidisciplinary research spanning engineering, social sciences, and humanities, the authors noticed differences in the conceptualization and operationalization of "trust" across practical and disciplinary settings in the context of data privacy and IoT devices. Upon conducting a review of trust definitions and discourses, we found divergences in where trust is located (in the system or in the user); whether trust is defined psychologically, emotionally, or functionally; and whether trust must involve risk. We also found that trust was sometimes discussed in a normative context as an end, in which trust was understood in connection with trustworthiness, and sometimes in a value-neutral way as a means, in which deserved and undeserved trust were not differentiated. Following our review of conceptualizations and operationalizations of trust in a data privacy context, we will present a critique and reformulation of "trust" based in disability studies, phenomenology, and feminist ethics of care. We find that trust is disfigured when regarded ahistorically and as inhering in either party rather than in the relationship between parties, since, if trust is not viewed as diachronic and negotiated, the moral force of betrayal cannot be accounted for. Since power is most visible at the margins, our analysis focuses on the privacy and trust experiences of BIPOC, women, disabled people, and LGBTQ people. Trust conceived in disconnection from trustworthiness amounts to compliance, and the uncritical use of "trust" when "compliance" is being addressed constitutes an ethics-washing that prevents an appropriate reckoning with the social impacts of emerging technology.

Creating epistemological contexts for culturally responsive research and practice in recovery *Kim McLeod, University of Tasmania*

Healthcare which enables recovery is responsive to cultural differences. Cultural difference is commonly theorised as an issue of stratification or identity, which limits accounting for how health care encounters produce difference. This presentation aims to further the epistemological contexts which enable culturally responsive research and practice in recovery. It critically examines relational ontologies and assemblage thinking in the empirical study of recovery, by asking, how do these conceptual and research practices produce difference? Drawing on

decolonial and ethical perspectives, the presentation shows how posthuman deployments of the 'relation' concept can erase or reveal difference. It advocates cultivating attention for cultural difference by making explicit a myriad of orientations to the relation concept - conceptual, methodological, ethical, political and bodily. The presentation contributes to debates about how STS scholarship deploys relational analytics. It expands conceptual and methodological approaches to research and practice in recovery.

Session Organizer:

Anne Pasek, Trent University

301. Demos, Tests, Prototypes - Politics of the not yet established

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

This panel discusses demos, tests, and patents as a class of experimental models and technologies that allow speculating within, on, and against societies. Whether dealing with financial markets, social networks, urban environments, or weather systems, multiple algorithmic systems and prototypes allow human beings to project and experience systems without fully controlling their further use. These are often sold as mere tests that take place within controlled settings. Yet, smart cities, machine learning systems, AVs and AIs are putting these very settings to the test, and thus exceed the frame that classic understandings of experiments and simulations proposed (Marres & Stark 2020). In similar ways, demos invoke wish images of the future and provide propensity for change, yet simultaneously preserve the current through its speculative prolongation into the future (Halpern 2021). Prototypes mark the becoming-technology of the demo and provide "socio-material devices for ordering the future in the present" (Wilkie 2010). The study of tests, demos, and prototypes reveals unsettled opportunities and abandoned imaginaries at the same time. We link our investigations into the political productivity of demos, tests, and patents to STS studies of experiments and simulations; at the same time, we want to emphasize the immediate epistemic and practical impact of experimental models and technologies by considering them as speculations against society. In the context of the Covid-19 pandemic, the hype around artificial intelligence, and the rising interest in algorithmic modeling of complex phenomena, we seek to scrutinize how experimental models and technologies (are imagined to) put our used-to understandings of politics and the social to the test. Halpern, Orit. 2021. "Demo", in *Uncertain Archives. Critical Keywords for Big Data*, ed. N. Thylstrup et al., 133-140. Marres, Noortje and David Stark. 2020. "Put to the test: For a new sociology of testing." *British Journal of Sociology* 71: 423-443. Wilkie, Alex. 2010. "Prototypes in Design: Materializing Futures". *LIMN 0: Prototyping Prototypes*. <https://limn.it/articles/prototypes-in-design-materializing-futures/>.

Participants:

The Perseverance Rover and Mediatization of Mars *Tero Karppi*, *University of Toronto*

Nasa's Mars 2020 Perseverance Rover is equipped with seven scientific instruments which include different kinds of cameras and imaging technologies from X-Ray system to panoramic camera and a spectrometer. It is carrying a mission to search for signs of past life on the planet and "test technologies to help pave the way for future human exploration of Mars". I propose that these two goals exemplify what Marres and Stark (2020) call a division between two scientific scenarios; the traditional, where testing happens "within a setting" and the contemporary, where the emphasis turns to "testing the setting". In this paper, I examine Mars Rover and its mission to prepare us for future planetary exploration as an example of the latter. In my analysis, I focus on the role of the media technologies carried by the Rover. I argue that the Rover is on a mission of "mediatization" (Couldy & Hepp 2013) where the aim is not only to produce more information about the planet but to change our orientation towards it and activate it "as an operation space" (Gabrys 2016). Couldry, Nick & Hepp, Andreas (2013), "Conceptualizing Mediatization: Contexts, Traditions, Arguments." *Communication Theory* 23: 191-202. Garbrys, Jennifer (2016).

Program Earth. University of Minnesota Press. Marres, Noortje and David Stark. 2020. "Put to the test: For a new sociology of testing." *British Journal of Sociology* 71: 423-443. Siegel, Greg (2016). *Forensic Media*. Duke University Press.

You Played Yourself: The Origins of World Politics as Computer Game *Fenwick McKelvey*, *Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA)*

In 1959, political scientist Oliver Benson created the first computer simulation of world politics. Written to run in the drum of an IBM 650 machine, Benson's Simple Diplomatic Game simulated international crises between nine nations. "Players" could read the print-outs if the United States declared all-out-war against the USSR (codename HBOMB). The simple game was a "modest beginning" that Benson thought had no utility for prediction. In spite of its humble origins, Benson was not the first nor the last to imagine the world as a game. Benson's slippage to describe international relations as a computer game has stabilized into a power socio-technical imaginary about politics and world order central to American defense intelligence. In 2020, the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency — what Sharon Weinberger calls the "imagineers of war" — announced a new program to support its work on military artificial intelligence, GAMEBREAKER (<https://www.darpa.mil/program/gamebreaker>). It trains a new generation of strategic AIs to master commercial computer games, presuming that masters these virtual competitions will port to predicting and defeating American opponents in the game of realpolitik. My presentation explores how it became sensible to imagine global politics as a computer game. The chapter focuses on the early prototypes that gradually legitimated system dynamic simulations of world politics to understand how a simple game led to GAMEBREAKER. Weinberger, Sharon. *The Imagineers of War: The Untold Story of DARPA, the Pentagon Agency That Changed the World*. Vintage, 2017.

Game Matches as Tests of Intelligence *Bart Simon*, *Concordia University, Montreal, Canada*

What is the kind of intelligence at work in a test match or a demo match of chess or Starcraft between a human player and a machine learning algorithm? On the one hand, the match is seen as a test of human-like or human-enough intelligence, on the other hand it is a demonstration of other-than-human capacity. But what does it mean to put gameplay to the test this way? At the root of the issue are legacy notions of gameplay as a form of idealized rational intelligence that sit at the heart of game theoretic assumptions about both human and machine behavior and their futures. This paper will consider the play of games from a broader sociological and game studies perspective and challenge the notion of intelligence that is being tested in these iconic matches. In doing so we may also ask what kind of gamers do we want our artificial intelligence to be?

Optimal Brain Damage. Theorizing the Nervous Present *Orit Halpern*, *Concordia University*; *Johannes Bruder*, *FHNW Academy of Art and Design*

This paper links a genealogy of models of population-based intelligence through the psychologist Donald O. Hebb, economist Friedrich Hayek, and perceptron inventor Frank Rosenblatt to contemporary efforts to model brains, societies, and other complex systems through neural nets. We argue that the forms of ecological cognition inherent to neural networks mingle conceptions of population-based intelligence and neo-liberal governance through a "neural imaginary". This idea—that the network could become the social, or conversely, that the social could become the network—arguably puts the very fabric of the social to the test (Marres & Stark 2020). These speculative "tests", now often conducted with planetary scale populations, have political and ethical implications for our present, for they increase volatility and precarity for many and lend themselves easily to contemporary reactionary politics. In our paper, we

exemplarily focus on “Optimal brain damage” (LeCun, Denker, Solla 1990)--an early pruning technique used to make artificial neural networks more efficient and resilient to shock and “trauma”--to explore the effects of technicalities on social interaction and democratic representation.

Session Organizer:

Johannes Bruder, FHNW Academy of Art and Design

Discussant:

Orit Halpern, Concordia University

302. Digital Data Collection and Migration Studies

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Participants:

Data Analytic Tools And Transnational Protest Movements:

Feminist Strategies Of Tracing Diasporic Digital Activism
Emily Edwards, Bowling Green State University; *Radhika Gajjala*, Bowling Green State University; *Sarah Ford*, Bowling Green State University

This paper examines feminist methodological strategies collecting data related to transnational protest movements involving diasporic activists. In this paper, we focus on the case study of protest against the Citizenship Amendment Act (CAA) and National Registry of Citizens (NRC), policies passed by the Indian government which limited citizenship to Hindus thereby marginalizing Muslim Indians. The CAA-NRC triggered protests in India, abroad, and on social media platforms. This paper examines archiving digital activism against the CAA-NRC, focusing specifically on materials related to protest leaders, the “Women of Shaheen Bagh,” who led a local protest movement from a working-class, Muslim neighborhood in Delhi. In this paper we examine the Shaheen Bagh protest as it was mediated on social media platforms such as Twitter and Instagram examining how the protest was portrayed; documenting connections between the Women of Shaheen Bagh and diasporic Indian activists in the United Kingdom as they sought to amplify the protests within the digital media landscape. Using the Shaheen Bagh protest as a case study we reflect on methods of data collection involving data scraping, data visualization, and Social Network Analysis (SNA). We consider how feminist researchers using data analytic tools approach issues of transnational activist coalitions, ethics of care in data collection processes, and preservation of marginalized voices within digital archival contexts. In this paper, we reflect upon data collection challenges and affordances of using data analytic tools to document, describe, and analyze a platformed, global protest that features transnational linkages that crossed religious, class, and caste lines.

Research on the move: WhatsApp as a tool for data collection with migrant populations *Thea de Gruchy*, University of the Witwatersrand

Reflecting global norms, South Africa is associated with high levels of cross-border and internal population mobility, yet migration-aware health system responses are lacking. One key methodological challenge limiting current research and, consequently, the development of evidence-informed responses to migration and health is the lack of methodologies that are able to capture ‘real-time’ data about health needs and healthcare seeking experiences over both time and place. This paper reflects on a four-month pilot project, which explored the use of WhatsApp Messenger, and assessed its feasibility as a research tool that would address this challenge. WhatsApp was used in conjunction with Survey Node, an online platform that allows for the automatic administration of surveys through WhatsApp, to administer monthly surveys to a group of 11 participants between October 2019 and January 2020. This paper uses the opportunities and challenges identified through the research as

the starting point from which to discuss the ethics and practicalities of digital research with migrant and mobile populations. The success of the pilot indicates that WhatsApp can be used as a tool for data collection with migrant and mobile populations. However, key practical and ethical challenges remain and require due consideration by researchers. Constant updates to WhatsApp, which affect both function and data security, require continuous assessment and adaptation by researchers. While WhatsApp provides numerous opportunities for research with migrant and mobile populations, particularly during the Covid19 pandemic, its ease and familiarity to researchers and participants alike requires additional measures to ensure that ethical standards are met.

Schools at the End of the World? Data, Salvage, and Online Learning *Anne Elizabeth Jonas*, UC Berkeley School of Information

Although hotly debated, when many schools shifted to remote learning in the face of the COVID-19 pandemic, the rationale was clear – to keep people safe while maintaining their access to education and employment. Without such a clear and present danger, many scholars and policy-makers harshly criticized pre-existing virtual schools as predatory vehicles to advance educational segregation for profit (e.g. Rooks 2017, Schneider and Berkshire 2020). Without debating the veracity of these allegations towards the developers of virtual schools, I argue that these organizations also make an appealing offer to prospective students, families, and teachers. Following the discussion of “interpretive resistance” by Crooks (2019), the performativity of digital data can create opportunities to contest centralized control, shifting the site of surveillance from the conditions of production to narrow outputs. By embracing datafication, then, virtual schools promise a measure of freedom that is particularly attractive to those who, for various reasons, chafe against rigid structures of standardization and will not, or cannot, conform. Online learning platforms translate the diverse labors of these teachers and students into commensurable units of data that they can then exchange for wages and credentials. Placing data from qualitative interviews and ethnographic observations around virtual schools in conversation with Tsing’s (2015) concept of “salvage” – “the freeing of inventory from production” – this paper analyzes how processes of data production can grant some forms of protection to data subjects, the costs associated with these practices, and their sustainability amidst the rapid expansion of digitization.

Session Organizers:

Negin Dahya, University of Toronto

Cansu Ekmekcioglu, University of Toronto

Chair:

Cansu Ekmekcioglu, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Negin Dahya, University of Toronto

303. Re-thinking And Experimenting With Participatory Research Practices And Design Through The Speculative And Ontological Turn - 1: Healthcare Practices and Ontology

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Compossibilities of a Never Event *Alex Wilkie*, Goldsmiths, University of London

A core assumption of multinaturalism is that different ‘cultures’ do not share the same ontological imagination or cosmology, but singular cultures do. In this paper I explore an auto-ethnographic case of an NHS ‘Never Event’, involving a serious instance of clinical negligence featuring the wrong-route administration of oramorph (oral morphine) during the emergency treatment of a hip fracture, and how this exposed different ontological

imaginings and possibilities (Deleuze, 2004) in both the immediate clinical experiences of the event as well as patient (non)involvement in the ensuing investigation. Echoing ethnographies of healthcare in which multiple ontologies necessarily co-exist and 'hang together' (Mol, 2003), the presentation probes the possibility that various possibilities, cosmologies and rationalities may be at play even within domains considered to have cosmological consistency and continuity.

Embedding spiritual care at home – 'Touching storytelling' and listening for difference *Sonja Jerak-Zuiderent, Amsterdam University Medical Centers; Janneke Vermeulen, The Athena Institute, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Carina Pittens, The Athena Institute, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam*

This paper explores the journey of our participatory system-oriented action research-based project working towards embedding 'spiritual care at home' in the Netherlands. The project follows from the policy by the Dutch Health Ministry to subsidize the provision of spiritual care not only within health care organisations, but also 'closer to home'. Relevant to the embedding of spiritual care the central theme emerged of 'the spiritual carer as entrepreneur' who is to reach out, via GPs or otherwise, into those homes. In this paper we explore the work it takes to practice 'good relations' with the 'other' project members and with practices of spiritual care in transition, when working together on the theme 'the spiritual carer as entrepreneur': What does it mean to do so from a speculative ethics perspective (Puig de la Bellacasa 2017), when all those involved in the project, from our different metaphysical commitments, move towards collective action that we all refer to as 'embedding spiritual care dynamically'? Drawing on a practice of embodied sensibility to unease and wonder in scholarly work (Jerak-Zuiderent, 2020), we explore how, 'touching storytelling' matters for rendering the differences among us with regards to this entrepreneurial notion not as absolute; but rather as an embodied practice of learning to be 'tactful' (Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017) to the metaphysical commitments of an 'other', by negotiating 'the possibility of disagreement' (Verran, 2014) when moving on together in embedding spiritual care, as done differently, at home.

The perpetual translation of developing inclusive vaccination guidelines *Teun Zuiderent-Jerak, Athena Institute, VU Amsterdam; Lea Loesch, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Elena Syurina, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Florian Kunneman, Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam; Aura Timen, National Institute for Public Health and the Environment (RIVM)*

The challenges of including experience-based knowledge and value considerations by patients and professionals in clinical practice guidelines (CPG) reflect conflicts of knowing and valuing in frequentist and other modes. We could take pains to describe these as ontologically multiple. But once again emphasizing such differences between the worlds epidemiologists and others make and do could render the prospects of 'integrating' knowledge from different worlds in a CPG rather gloomy. Not a luxury we can afford in an experimental collaboration between the Dutch Institute for Public Health and the Environment, a Social AI research group, and a group of STS researchers. We have taken up the challenge to investigate the role AI technologies may play in innovating the inclusion of values and experiential knowledges in vaccination guidelines, including for Covid-19, to ensure CPGs have a 'better performance in the field'. We explore how AI-based methods may innovatively enact citizens' and health professionals' experiences and value judgements and translate them into robust knowledge that can be integrated into the development of vaccination guidelines through participatory methods. We attend guideline development meetings, mobilise text mining to analyse

existing but unexplored sets of textual records containing societal and professional knowledge and concerns are expressed, and organize frame reflection workshops where we, guideline developers, and other knowers become involved in making knowledge integration productive despite ontological divergences (Ludwig, 2016). If we manage, even remotely, what does this teach us about the prospects for 'overthrowing ontology' and placing ourselves – and others – into "perpetual translation" (Serres, 1991)?

Session Organizer:

Peter Danholt, Aarhus University

304. Technology, Aesthetics, and the Body - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

People are increasingly tasked with both the aesthetic and scientific management and optimization of their bodies. For women and non-binary people, in particular, "health" and "beauty" are not simply individual achievements, but comprise the terrain in which battles over the "fitness of the race and the nation" have been played out (Strings 2019:194). Technologies from X-ray machines to Fitbits are mobilized in these fights. STS has analyzed how gender and racial ideologies are embedded within such technologies. This panel draws attention to technologies of the body with a particular eye toward aesthetics. How does the body become articulated, legible, and fortified through the use of technology? We are especially interested in everyday, mundane objects that have often not been analyzed as technologies, such as cosmetics, clothing, and accessories. Technologies of embodiment like cosmetics have been dismissed as commodities or frivolities. But subjects use them to resist subordination and to express themselves in ways that can subvert oppression at personal and structural scales. We invite submissions of papers about technologies of embodiment, enhancement and adornment, especially on the following subjects: -The disruption of the binary between natural and artificial -The enforcement of the gender binary, heteronormativity, and transmisogyny -The construction or disruption of racial and colonial formations -The political economy of makeup -Fashion -Beauty gurus and social media influencers -Cosmetic surgery -DIY body and "bio" hacking

Participants:

#DeGenderFashion Alok Vaid-Menon, Rutgers University

From the 1840s until the 1970s (and in some cases later) "masquerade" or "cross-dressing" laws criminalized people for wearing articles of clothing associated with the "other sex" in the US. While anti-cross dressing legislation may no longer appear on the books, it still structures our aesthetic, academic, and political imagination. At the peak of anti-cross dressing legislation in the early 20th century, people perceived as women wearing pants were maligned by the press, harassed in public, even criminalized and arrested. Due to the work of feminist dress reformers, in the 21st century the figure of "women in pants" no longer solicits the same form of scrutiny and aspersion. Nonetheless, the figure of a "man in a dress" still incites extreme backlash and societal consternation. What underlies our ability to acknowledge pants as gender neutral, and our refusal to recognize a dress as gender neutral? What do these investments teach us about gender and fashion as both potentially disciplinary and liberatory modalities? In this paper I approach fashion as a technology to think through questions of race, labor, and gender to understand how the colonial gender binary comes to be designed. In centering questions of style and aesthetic embodiment, what is so often dismissed as ornamental becomes instrumental: I reveal transmisogyny as a constitutional force for notions of progress and civilization.

The Cyborg as Grottesquerie: Disability, Aesthetics, and the Other Joshua Earle, Virginia Tech

Cyborg imagery generally falls into two camps. Either the image depicts an idealized human form with some aesthetically-pleasing artificiality, or it shows a bodymind corrupted by technology; hideous, grotesque, and to be avoided. In this talk I

argue that the cyborg as grotesquerie -- and the horror that such images seek to evoke -- are based in longstanding ableist tropes that both dehumanize disabled people, and depict any attempt to use technology to overcome disability as an affront to the "natural" or as an act of hubris. Messages like this abound in Science Fiction and gaming (where most cyborg imagery resides) and is perhaps best exemplified by the Warhammer 40k universe, or any number of body horror science fiction and cyberpunk worlds. In this talk I dig into the history of bodyminds as grotesquerie, and discuss how this history informs the images and descriptions of cyborg bodyminds. From Eugenics and Ugly Laws, to Freak Shows and Circus Oddities, to the rise of cosmetic and reconstructive surgery after the American Civil War, the cyborg grotesquerie exemplifies both a fear of the overreach of science toward the unnatural, and the distrust of bodyminds whose appearance runs counter to our expectations. I challenge us to consider another way, one that values difference as generative of new possibilities, where the grotesque and the apotheosis work together to unlock potential bodymind arrangements, and fights back against ableism and fear of the other.

Bedazzle, Inscribe, Flaunt: The Personal Resistance Practices of People Required to Wear Electronic Ankle Monitors *Lauren Kilgour, Princeton University*

Electronic ankle monitors are a type of wearable technology that enable continuous geo-temporal government surveillance in domains such as criminal justice (e.g. probation, parole, and pretrial supervision) and immigration (e.g. as an alternative to immigration detention centers). People who are required to wear electronic ankle monitors frequently express that they experience shame and stigmatization as a result of being required to wear this technology, due to its strong association with the criminal justice system. I describe and analyze the cultures of resistance that circulate in response to electronic ankle monitor design and use in the United States. My analysis is based on ethnographic and social media research conducted between 2016-2020. My research reveals that people required to wear electronic ankle monitors create and circulate cultural representations of electronic ankle monitors that seek to re-shape and alter public perceptions of the technology's symbolic meaning, without disrupting their technological operation. Put directly, wearers craft aesthetic interventions that reclaim the "form factor" (the physical look and feel of computing technology) of ankle monitors, seeking to transform it from a site of stigma to a site of resistance. This research traces the broader social consequences of using electronic ankle monitors to augment community-based supervision, and whether the design of such technologies actually meet the social and policy objectives driving their creation and use. Ethical technology design and use urgently depends upon centering and elevating the voices, acts, and experiences of people and communities rendered vulnerable by technology design and deployment.

The Queer Afterlives of Postwar Plastics *Isabelle Held, Science History Institute*

Today binders; packers; breast, hip and butt pads are made of plastics originally developed via WWII industrial and military materials research. Plastics surround us in our everyday interactions, but we give little thought to their provenance. This paper traces the political, industrial and military origins of the plastics found in these queer objects. It follows the peacetime plasticity of their postwar corporeal applications in the US, exploring how these materials have been used in relation to the body to both uphold and subvert racialized gender norms. Nylon, unveiled by explosives manufacturer DuPont in 1939, was the world's first fully synthetic fiber. After being co-opted for military equipment including parachutes it was launched on the domestic market as stockings. Today nylon blends and derivatives, including Lycra, are used in binders, like those produced by Black/Latinx trans-owned gc2b. Plastic foams made

of wartime synthetic rubber substitutes developed for military applications were later molded into 3D objects and used to augment the body via "falsies", padded foundationwear and implants. Silicone, an engine lubricant developed to aid the US war effort, was later used in cosmetics and aesthetic body contouring. Praised for its ability to mimic flesh, silicones found a new home in medical devices, prosthetics and sex toys. This paper offers a queer history of plastics as well as their technological transfer, subversion and role in shaping corporealities. It contributes to STS by synthesizing histories of science, technology, medicine and gender studies with an attention to artifacts and materials found within design histories.

Beauty Matters: Cosmetic Surgery, Race, and Technologies of Adornment *Alka Menon, Yale University*

Racial and gender identities can be signaled through fashion, comportment, and, with the advent of increasing access to aesthetic medicine, modified physical features. This paper analyzes cosmetic surgery as a technology of beauty that produces race and gender as material and embodied entities. It argues that technologies related to beauty and the body are a critical part of the architecture of racial meaning, providing insight into the semiotics of race that would be missed with a focus on state-of-the-art developments in science. In cosmetic surgery, a now-longstanding technology, patients and cosmetic surgeons can use the tools of medicine to make racial identities embodied. This adopts the logic of Donna Haraway's cyborg, "a cybematic organism, a hybrid of machine and organism...who populate[s] worlds ambiguously natural and crafted." Embracing the possibility of self-authorship and hybridity, Haraway paves the way for recognizing prosthetics, implants, and surgical interventions in pursuit of a deliberately fashioned identity. Like other embodied technologies (e.g., pacemakers and wearables), beauty technologies such as makeup, clothing, and cosmetic surgery are comparatively low-tech, small-scale, and even mundane: the kinds of ordinary and familiar technologies STS scholarship sometimes neglects. Challenging the view that beauty is unimportant and frivolous, this paper expands STS scholarship by analyzing technologies of adornment, with an eye toward their implications for race and gender. Narratives and counter-narratives of beauty technologies shed light on the enduring relevance of race and gender in biomedicine.

Session Organizer:

Alok Vaid-Menon, Rutgers University

Chair:

Alka Menon, Yale University

305. After Normal: Establishing Normality (Panel One of Two)

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

In retrospect, the 20th century may have been the Century of the Normal. The normal and its variations—the normate, the normative, the norm, and normality—have guided scholarly attention to institutions, processes of subjectivity, categories of personhood, and everyday interactions. As a set of heuristics, the normal and its variations helped to point attention toward racist, ableist, sexist, and homophobic biases in medical and scientific practice, in governance, in institutional arrangements, and throughout society—in the North Atlantic and elsewhere. But what happens after the normal? If the early 21st century has demonstrated anything, it is that the normal is not what it used to be as a heuristic or set of practices. Maybe this is the downstream effect of two decades of debate around postmodernism, liquid modernity, and performative drag; maybe this is a function of norm-breaking political movements, nationally and globally. Maybe the erosion of the normal is an effect of the waves of intersectional and identity critiques that dislodged cisgendered, able-bodied, heterosexual, middle class whiteness from its foundational basis as the normal. Or maybe it is the effect of scholarly attention to already existing communities refusing or practicing normality according to their own logics. Scholars working at the intersections of science and technology studies, critical race theory, disability studies, and within feminist and anti-colonial frameworks have

been critical here. Entering into 2021, it is fair to say that we are “after normal.” But where does that leave us? The normal still pervades medicine, science, and everyday life. What tools have science and technology scholars uncovered for articulating a move away from the normal and its legacies? How might we—individually and collectively—reconceptualize the basis of normalcy from insights provided by ethnographic, archival, and other empirical work that exposes the fissures in the normal and its powers? Panel 1: Staging Normalcy This panel is organized around normalcy as a set of discourses that has developed in specific historical and contemporary contexts and the work that such discourses do.

Participants:

When was normal? How the old Jim Crow created the new Normal *Laura Stark, Vanderbilt University*

Starting in 1954 through 1980, the US National Institutes of Health recruited seemingly healthy civilians as “normal control” research subjects for the government’s in-house medical experiments. NIH administrators and scientists called these people Normals, and they used productively inconsistent criteria to determine who was normal—and who was not. At a 1957 staff conference, NIH researchers identified three forms of normalcy, which chime with the definitions of normalcy critically analyzed by Canguilhem, Foucault, and others: normalcy defined by statistics, by an individual’s optimum, or by “relevance,” that is, a lack of pathology in the specific area under study. Yet the NIH Normals had one thing in common: they were all White. The goal of this paper is to explore specific organizational strategies and collective actions that offer present and future possibilities for dismantling racist norms in bioscience. To that end, the paper studies the chronicity of the Normal to ask: When was Normal? In doing so, the paper unfurls the premise of the session—that there was a moment after which experts in the dominant biomedical sciences recognized their definitions of normalcy were political statements, not only scientific parameters. “After normal” marks the period when the definition of the Normal, as a medico-legal technology, could no longer function as a Latourian black box: when the power relations that configured the material arrangements could no longer pass by without caveat or question. In exploring this case, the paper witnesses what was accomplished in the period of the Normal, when multiple, incompatible definitions of normalcy flourished under the modern administrative state. Specifically, the paper shows how the organizations through which NIH recruited Normals had racist practices of exclusions themselves—including colleges, labor unions, churches, and civic groups. As a result, in its apolitical foils, the multiple normalcies at NIH were defined by the White body. Research with any other groups were set in field sites, not hospitals, and related to pathology, not used to establish the bounds of normalcy. Because of this organizational practice, the time of the Normal yielded an enduring assumption that to be Normal was to be White; that to be Black or Brown was to be deviant. The aim of the paper is to invite conversation about organizational practices and collective action.

The nature of normal: disability and kinship in urban Jordan *Christine Sargent, University of Colorado, Denver*

This paper traces how women raising children with Down syndrome in urban Jordan mobilized secular and religious models of causality to challenge ableist framings of disability as “abnormal.” Care networks in Jordan rely on gendered distributions of re/productive labor, which in turn takes shape through assessments of normality. Impairment and disability both illuminate and unsettle these investments in being “normal,” and families adopt different tactics to accommodate and protect the sanctity of their status as such. Strategically playing with the semantic overlaps between natural and normal, the women with whom I conducted fieldwork stressed that all forms of human diversity reflect the intentionality of divine creation. Given God’s oneness (tawhid), equating Down syndrome with abnormality amounted to a morally significant breach of misrecognition; God doesn’t make mistakes. In a similar line of argument, many

women claimed their children’s equality before God and challenged pervasive disability stigma by locating all human beings in a shared genealogy as “children of Adam.” While women also drew on a wealth of medical and biogenetic information to contradict stereotypes and misconceptions about Down syndrome, the ambiguity and open-endedness of these resources relied on reinforcement by shared truths about human nature and God’s power. While families and advocates utilized new framings and networks of disability to negotiate with the hegemony of normality, they did not necessarily dispute the value of normal. Instead, they sought to reconfigure its boundaries. Ultimately, this paper advocates for ethnographically informed accounts of how the normal and the nonsecular (Roberts and Whitmarsh 2016) remain deeply entangled, even as they respond to shifting social norms and values.

Assessing “normal hearing” with cochlear implants *Stephanie Lloyd, Université Laval*

“Most young audiologists I work with have never seen a deaf child who can’t talk.” This is how an Australian clinical audiologist who had worked closely with the team that had developed one of the first commercialized cochlear implants (CIs) summarized the experiences of professionals in her field in 2018. Clinical audiology literature supports this statement, suggesting that many people with CIs can test “normally” based on assessments of hearing using pure tones and single sounds in audiometric booths. Furthermore, the speech of many people with CIs is indistinguishable from their typical hearing peers. However, a significant literature also suggests that the hearing of people with CIs is different than that of their typical hearing peers. Different, in this case, includes (1) difficulties hearing in loud environments or situations with multiple speakers, and (2) use of different sensory inputs and neurocognitive processes to hear, as compared to typical hearers. What, then, counts as normal? Where (audiometric booth, day to day environments)? According to what measures? Moreover, does “normal” correspond to outcomes measures (e.g., speech, standard tests) or the biological-technological processes that lead to an outcome, and what if one is “normal” (the former) and the other is not (the latter), according to standards of “normal hearing”? In this paper, I will examine the diversity underlying “normal hearing” with CIs, ask what normal renders invisible, and consider why it matters when normal displaces questions of how people get there.

Health justice beyond the race-unconscious normal in the French/Caribbean *Raphaelle Rabanes, University of Washington Seattle*

What is the normal when equity is a future kept out of reach in the postcolony? In the French Caribbean territory of Guadeloupe, health professionals and patients navigate an older university health center in perpetual crisis even as they await the inauguration of a new hospital. The situation is typical of the overseas department, where projects routinely stall, leaving postcolonial subjects in “bigidi,” stumbling to cobble care at the margins of the French system. Based on 18 months of fieldwork at the readaptation clinic of a large Guadeloupean hospital, I define a model of postcolonial repair from the margins of normalcy. Expanding on the Disability Critical Race Theory scholarship in the US, I approach concerns of inequities in health access in the broader context of the afterlives of slavery. I detail clinical realities shaped by a long history of racialized treatment in post-slavery societies. Turning to the efforts of Guadeloupean health actors, I examine their demands for health justice and postcolonial repair. I explore the institutional work required to defend readaptation in the projects of the new hospital where beds are projected to be reduced and long-term stays of readaptation contradict the emphasis on outpatient care. As health workers battle the new hospital project, they refuse the managerial logic of 21st-century care. Instead, they assert an alternate vision of normalcy grounded in an anti-colonial stance.

Criminalization as Disability *Jennifer Lieberman, University of North Florida*

Like the other disciplinary institutions that panelists will discuss in our series, the prison is a space that relies on the undefinable, overdetermined, and ableist idea of the normal. In the carceral state, the normal is often invoked negatively rather than affirmatively: when victims or their families imagine that they can “return to normal” only after an offender is found and punished; or when Americans accept the idea that “normal” or “average” Americans won’t be incarcerated. Even the progressive, reformist paradigm of the prison draws on medicalized ideas about rehabilitation that imagine coercing abnormal bodies back to normalcy. In this paper, I trace how the normal/abnormal binary shapes stakeholders’ discussions about prisons, historically and presently. I contend that the idea of normal, perfectible people and normal, perfectible punishment is used to legitimate the prison’s continued growth and existence, and, reciprocally, that notions about criminals as abnormal serve to reinforce ableist discourses beyond the prison. My methodology is historicist discourse analysis, studying the way that states, wardens, incarcerated people, and popular culture represents the criminal mind as a type of disability, and tracing how these discourses have evolved throughout the twentieth century.

Session Organizer:

Michele Friedner, The University Of Chicago

Chair:

Matthew Wolf-Meyer, Binghamton University

306. Situating, transforming, and (de)centering Images of the Futures - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Our current realities are a mess to embrace: the current global pandemic and its disruptions in labor, education, and other socio-technical systems; the increasing political and ontological polarizations and the urgent action against a human-catalyzed climate emergence are challenged our notion of safety, certainty, and even the survival of life on earth (as the ongoing massive extinction, and other fateful events). Our cartesian imaginations in fiction, planning, modeling, anticipation, and foresight are being defied for the unknown, opening a public demand for new ecological, material, and inter-mutual relations around the globe. A source of these imaginations are images of the future. In 1961, Frederick Polak defined it as “images of the totally other, and they are revolutionary and radical in nature, or they are nothing at all”. Future studies have contributed to popularize these images, (Inayatullah, 2008; Zheltikova & Khokhlova, 2019), which are connected to the movements of decolonial anthropologies and designs (Tlostanova, 2017; Escobar, 2018; Schultz, 2018), as well offer powerful insight for the study of emergent socio-technical imaginaries (Jasanoff, 2015; Konrad & Böhle, 2019). This panel wants to set a conversation around the role of images of the future in STS, in particular projects and practices looking at local, topical, or systemic images. We hope to have contributions to understanding how to situate, expand, nuance, and (de)centered “images of the futures”, to produce alternative realities (like Afro-futurism or Solar-Punk), and to restore more-than-human balances from the unequal, unbalanced, and unfair relations across scales.

Participants:

Generic Techno-Visions of the Future: Exploring the Visual Rhetoric of ‘Futuristic’ Stock Images *Anneli Bowie, University of Johannesburg*

This paper explores the aesthetics and rhetorics of commercial stock images categorised as communicating the concept of ‘the future’. Stock images may be considered the ‘wallpaper of consumer culture’ (Frosh) but also as ‘central to the ambient image environment that defines our visual world’ (Aiello). One could argue that conceptual stock images visualising abstract notions of ‘the future’ form a major part of our globalised futural vocabulary and that we need to scrutinize these images for their

explicit and implied framings. Through their ubiquity, these images may have major impacts on how we imagine the future, and, I would argue, can potentially hinder the development of alternative, more imaginative ‘socio-technical imaginaries’. In this paper, I consider how the visual logic of stock images, centred largely on the market-driven production of generic and polysemic potentiality, influences how ‘the future’ is visualised: in conventional/conservative, decontextualized and non-descript terms. I aim to illustrate this argument by analyzing the visual rhetorical tactics of the most popular ‘futuristic’ stock images on two major stock image platforms, namely iStock (by Getty Images) and Shutterstock. I interrogate both visual content and form/style in order to identify prominent metaphorical clusters or themes. I conclude by considering the broader significance and implications of these dominant visual framings of ‘the future’, particularly in light of the need to develop decolonized and locally-appropriate futural visions.

Precog Visions: Predicting the Future of the Sociotechnical Imaginaries of Minority Report *Mehitabel Glenhaber, University of Southern California; Hamsini Sridharan, Annenberg School for Communication & Journalism, University of Southern California*

We interrogate the politics behind claims that science fiction “predicts the future” through a case study of how the 2002 film *Minority Report* has been hailed by “tech beats” such as *Wired Magazine* as a triumph of technological forecasting. We explore the relationship between fictional and “realized” technologies, arguing that the sociotechnical imaginaries encoded in sci-fi visions of the future are adopted piecemeal by different audiences in the imagination, construction, and contestation of “real-world” technologies (Jasanoff, 2015a, 2015b). In our analysis of discourse about three technologies featured in *Minority Report* (gesture tech, targeted advertising, and “PreCrime”), we find that tech writers selectively remember or misremember aspects of the film’s futuristic vision, emphasizing technical gadgetry and marginalizing issues of race, gender, and carceral politics. They overstate the successful realization of some technologies depicted in the film, while glossing over others (e.g. futuristic prisons, crack-cocaine-coded drugs, cyborg woman psychics). Furthermore, when *Minority Report* is invoked in tech news, the film’s world is remembered as containing a different set of technologies and social concerns than when it is invoked in mainstream publications or activist statements. Our findings complicate Kirby’s theory of “diegetic prototyping” (2010), which may occlude the multiplicity of voices in the film’s worldbuilding design process and public reactions (Pendleton-Jullian and Brown, 2018). We demonstrate how audiences select elements from a film’s vision of the future in order to craft sociotechnical imaginaries and make political claims about whether their own imaginary is close to the world we live in now.

Reconfiguring anticipatory knowledge systems - a case of energy futures and disruptive transition *Joshua Loughman, SFIS - Arizona State University*

Futures are a natural concern for Science and Technology Studies (STS) as they do work to both engage decision-making about the present and they enable or disable alternative sociotechnical system pathways. Actors in sociotechnical systems mobilize futures by incorporating them into their anticipatory knowledge systems. These visions of the future are shaped by institutional and social inertias as well as by disruptions. This research examines a case of an energy utility situated at such an inertia-disruption juncture and explores how the actors in this case reconfigured their anticipatory knowledge system. Stabilized visions of the future are seen in this case as focused on “engineering resilience” while the reconfigured system adapts to the external disruption of changing energy technology and economic pressures by adopting an “ecosystem resilience”

approach. This change in perspective is coproduced with a change in anticipation. At the core of this project is understanding how system change or the anticipation of system change alters the ways affected actors in the sociotechnical system adopt new future-oriented techniques in response. The questions addressed by this research are an extension of the Winnerian question of whether technology has politics. In what ways do our futures have politics? The shaping of futures by the social contexts and discourses are in turn shaping the decisions and strategies that are made and allowed to be considered within sociotechnical systems. Understanding how futures are reconfigured by sociotechnical system transition provides important insights for responsible research and innovation, anticipatory governance, and transition studies.

Silicon Fantasies or Baroque Dreams? *Alexander Wentland, Technical University of Munich*

After the German Reunification, the city of Dresden has reinvented itself as the European leader in microelectronics, often referred to as “Silicon Saxony” but also as the “Florence on the Elbe” because of its Baroque architecture. However, despite its role as a poster child for a successful transition from planned to market economy, phantom pain plagues the city. Dresden is stuck in a glorified tourist vision of its past, a struggle for conservation, in which a modern future is unimaginable, because the promises of modernity have been shattered by the collapse of the German Democratic Republic. Decades before that, Dresden’s citizens have witnessed the physical collapse of their city under the bombardment of the Allied Forces in WW2, months before the German NS regime capitulated. These two ruptures of societal order are still haunting a city that likes to present itself as an S&T hub that punches way above its league. I argue that the harsh sociomaterial breaks of 1945 and 1989, particularly the way they are distorted or suppressed today, have created a situation of temporal dislocation. Empirically, I trace specific sites and initiatives that try to reconcile Dresden’s past, present, and future through the imaginary of innovation, while new specters of Soviet nostalgia and right wing populism are invading into the same traumatic timescape.

Promising a Future / Building a Present through automated vehicle advertisements *Jameson Wetmore, Arizona State University*

Since governments have largely been sitting on the sidelines in the development of automated vehicles in the United States, corporations have been playing a major role in preparing the public for a future with a new transportation system. This study analyzes the ways in which AV companies are using video advertisements to sell their specific visions of an automated future. Taken together, the images promoted in these venues demonstrate that there is a wide variety of sociotechnical arrangements being proposed. Despite the talk of “a future with self driving cars,” numerous different possible futures are being independently developed. At the same time the messages embedded in these images demonstrate that the companies involved know they have an uphill battle in getting both the general public and prospective customers to embrace their vision and they are using a variety of techniques to make their preferred futures seem both obvious and necessary. This talk will review the different proposed futures being presented to illustrate the tensions between them as well as review the strategies used to build support for their futures.

Session Organizer:

Martin Andrés Perez Comisso, SFIS - Arizona State University

Discussant:

Dayna Jeffrey, Department of Science & Technology Studies, York University

307. Un/Making a Difference 5: borders, boundaries, ethics, work & systems

9:40 to 11:10 am
4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Participants:

Contestation designs: material (re)configurations of a borderscape *Silvia Mata-Marin, Universidad de Costa Rica*

The project of modernity reordered and rearranged the world by imposing categories of difference. These categories of difference materialize in inconspicuous bordering systems designed to enforce the separation between the Global North and Global South; the west and rest; the have and have-nots: dualities continuously (re)produced today in the spatial arrangement of the world and in the domain of everyday life. These categories, rooted in colonial logic of difference, give shape and structure to a place like Río Azul, a marginal, urban neighborhood in the outskirts of San Jose, Costa Rica, inhabited by a large population of undocumented Nicaraguan migrants. Río Azul can be understood as a borderzone or borderscape, a site where cultural difference is asserted, contained, and (re)enforced (Mezzandra and Neilson, 2013). This is the site where many undocumented migrants carry out their everyday lives as an orchestrated set of practices that enable them to reappropriate and work around the sociotechnical systems that make up the “the existential conditions of migrants who are always dwelling in the borders” (Mignolo 2000). In the face of state exclusion, undocumented migrants, resort to practices which can be referred to as “migrant counterconducts” (Inda, 2011) defined as “acts or forms of comportment that contest the criminalization and exclusion of the undocumented.” (Inda & Dowling, 2013). These counterconducts can range everywhere from organized political action such as protesting to everyday forms of resistance that respond directly to their dwelling conditions and materialize in designs and infrastructure intended to provide the possibilities to carry out everyday life processes while the imposition of the undocumented condition actively and explicitly disallows these processes. Based on the experience of undocumented Nicaraguan women who dwell in Río Azul, this paper presents the concept of contestation designs through an exploration of the kinds of designs that emerge from “the encounter with given realities (actualities, situations, circumstances, conditions or experiences)” and that are materialized “in terms of their transformative possibilities and potentialities” (Dilnot, 2005) by undocumented women as a tactical reversibility of power intended to contest state and state-delegated power to reshape Río Azul to allow for the reproduction of life. This paper presents the concept of contestation designs as part of the repertory that opens the understanding of design to consider how other logics that emanate from the subjectivities of the Global South materialize in the forms of design for survival and designs intended for autonomy (Escobar, 2018).

"Why Is Our Profession Like This?": Challenging Academic (Over)work Norms *Rosemary Steup, Indiana University*

It is an open secret that academia has a culture of overwork, and that the harms of this culture often fall on early-career researchers, marginalized groups, and those with caregiving responsibilities. Given the widespread awareness of this problem, some academics have tried to push back against norms of overwork and instead model a healthy relationship with work for their peers and students. However, what constitutes a healthy or sustainable work arrangement is different for different people and will change over the course of a person’s life. In trying to combat overwork, we risk labeling as unhealthy any work arrangement that doesn’t fit the standard model, whether or not it actually is healthy for the person engaging in it. The conversation about overwork in academia is tied into many broad questions about power and privilege: who has control over their time; who can afford to work less/more; what kinds of labor are recognized and valued in academic spaces; and more. Based on qualitative analysis of posts on Academic Twitter—one public venue in

which the debate about academic overwork is unfolding—I attempt to map the discursive positions being taken in this conversation. What sorts of work arrangements are people advocating? How do they define overwork? Where are people clashing, and what conflicting assumptions do they hold? Understanding the discursive space is key to learning how we as academics can more effectively support each other and how to continue this conversation in constructive and non-harmful ways.

Teacherly Response-ability: Care-As-Protest Against Violent Relations in Mathematics Education *Grace A. Chen*

Critical scholars argue that mathematics education is characterized by violent, unjust, and dehumanizing relations, especially for historically marginalized students. How, then, can mathematics teachers who value the humanity and wellbeing of their students—yet are inextricably complicit in the infrastructures of mathematics education—be in right relation? Drawing on ethnographically-collected data and poststructural analyses, I examine how two secondary mathematics teachers care, as a form of protest, about what the cultures and norms of mathematics education do not care about: the complex agencies, affects, histories, and contexts in which mathematics education, mathematics teachers, and mathematics students are entangled. In the spirit of diffraction (Barad, 2007), I find patterns of difference that make a difference between these teachers' ethical stances on relational work and the claims made by commonsensical notions of good and equitable mathematics teaching about getting to know students, cultivating classroom climates, and preparing students for the future. These patterns of difference call attention to how teachers could navigate their institutional power and interpret and invite students' agency differently, and to the promise of an ethics of response-ability for enacting more just versions of mathematics education. I offer these teachers' stories as humble examples of Shotwell's (2016) "do what we can—recognizing that what we can do, on its own, will never be enough" with the hope that they might spark imaginations and open up possibilities about the narratives, metaphors, and pedagogical practices we take for granted in mathematics education.

The Politics of Resistance and Everyday Negotiations: A Case Study of Rohingya Community in India *Madhusree Jana, Jawaharlal Nehru University (JNU) India*

Most South Asian countries lack a legal framework for refugee management, and India is no exception. Despite experiencing refugee influxes over the past several decades, the Indian government has maintained an ad-hoc approach in dealing with asylum seekers. Moreover, the lack of cooperation between the State and non-state actors often leaves the refugee communities in a socio-legal vacuum. As a result, the refugee communities are faced with discriminatory practices in accessing the job market, education, and healthcare. Focusing on the Rohingya refugee community in India, this paper aims to shed light on the everyday negotiations and practices the refugees perform to create spaces for a secure livelihood, both inside and outside the community. This study is based on a field survey undertaken in Delhi, Haryana, and Uttar Pradesh during September 2020 and February 2021. Relying on demographic and socioeconomic information collected via in-depth interviews (n=207), this paper investigates how the lack of state assistance serves as an impetus for the refugees to carve out personal protection spaces and devise livelihood mechanisms. While the regressive citizenship policies (the Citizenship Amendment Act, for instance) of the current Indian State have attributed to further suffering of the stateless Rohingya population and failed to address the legal vacuum for refugees, the livelihood strategies developed by the refugee population nonetheless are important markers of resistance and self-reliance; and have the potential to contribute to the dialogue of refugee protection.

User Experience Professionals' Work Addressing Values and

Ethics as Soft Resistance *Richmond Y Wong, University of California, Berkeley*

This paper investigates the labor of user experience (UX) professionals who work at large North American technology companies, and attempt to re-configure how their companies approach issues related to social values and ethics from their positions within the boundaries of their professional roles. I describe these attempts at re-configuration while working from within as a form of everyday and mundane resistance work. This includes utilizing tactics that aspire to: create more space for UX professionals to address ethics in their everyday work; make ethics visible and legible to other organizational stakeholders; and change organizational processes. Yet, these tactics of everyday resistance often rely on the dominant discourses and logics of Silicon Valley and the technology industry. While these resistance practices and resulting re-configurations may be characterized as partial or "soft," this work nevertheless involves navigating forms of precarity and conducting emotional labor, while attempting to imagine alternative re-configurations from within systems of power. Through interviews with North American UX professionals and observations at UX meetup events in the San Francisco Bay Area, this work builds on values in design research that seeks to study how values are implicated in the relationships among humans and technical artifacts, and create interventions to address values and ethics during the design process. My findings are accompanied by the presentation of "design fiction memos," conceptual and speculative design artifacts that I created to reflect on and analyze the qualitative data, and as a way to articulate and communicate insights.

Session Organizer:

Kat Jungnickel, Goldsmiths, University of London

Chair:

Carl DiSalvo

308. Caste as/of Technoscience - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Despite its continued importance as an analytical category in the social life of south asia, and south asians globally, caste as a lens or a category of analysis has historically remained relatively undertheorized in the social studies of science and technology. If at all, caste has largely figured as an identity category in extant work. Can reframing the study of caste as a study of technoscience improve our engagements with caste as a social category as well as that of the social study of science and technology? What conceptual and methodological toolkit would such a move need? How are caste and technoscience intertwined? Is caste an historically morphing assemblage which shapeshifts as new sociotechnical arrangements become possible/are enabled by it? If so, what new ways of thinking about caste are enabled when we approach 'caste' as technoscience? And vice versa, what new ways of thinking about technoscience are enabled as we think about 'technoscience' as caste? This panel invites papers that work with caste not only in axes of identity vis a vis technoscientific worlds but also think through caste as technoscience. These may range from case studies of sociotechnical assemblages that converge around different kinds of "work," debates around labour and caste relations, discursive efforts towards castelessness in the name of "merit," to theoretical pieces that reflect on methodological concerns on the matter which address the co-construction and reification of the caste system through technoscientific practices, imagination and rhetoric in different communities of South Asia and its diaspora.

Participants:

Caste, Technology and Untouchability: An Enquiry into the Co-Production of Technology in the Practice of Manual Scavenging *Kanthi Swaroop, Centre for Policy Studies, IIT Bombay*

When the practice of manual scavenging was outlawed by the government of India in 2013, it emphasized technology among the other more common solutions prescribed to abolish it. Vital

to the well-being of Indian cities, sewage work has proven hazardous and all too often fatal for its labor force—a problem at the intersection of public health, infrastructural development, and India’s controversial yet enduring social order: caste. Here, sanitation workers are made to labor in extreme hazardous conditions with rudimentary equipment, often described as the practice of manual scavenging — a primitive caste-based practice identical to practices of untouchability — forcing predominantly the Dalit (ex-untouchables) castes to manually clean insanitary latrines, manholes, sewers, and septic tanks. Eight years have passed since government of India proscribed this practice, however, manual scavenging is neither abolished nor there is deployment of technology. One reason is that government and anti-manual scavenging activists share competing views over technology thus, preventing an opportunity for co-production of technology to emerge, despite historically, “co-production”, a particular strand of STS been proven successful in finding solutions to complex social problems by its knowledge production capacity while interacting with technology and social order. How does caste order control the experiences of technology? Is it because, the caste order — a social hierarchy which structures, defines, and reproduces laboring in a particular way opposes the introduction of technology for its latent potentiality in altering the social relations? This article, thus problematizes absence of co-production: scientists neither work at the sites where manual scavengers labor nor do they invite manual scavengers to their laboratories to develop technological solutions which will help to tackle the practice of manual scavenging. Grounded in ethnographic evidence, this paper argues that absence of co-production is the result of dalitness of sanitation work, and the stigmatized laboring of manual scavengers. Approaching from the theory of co-production this article develops preliminary ideas towards the interconnectedness of caste, technology and untouchability.

The Scientific Life in British India, 1915-20 *Charu Singh, Stanford University*

In the early twentieth century, the life of science was novel to most colonial subjects in British India. Who a scientist was, what they did, what particular skills and virtues were required for becoming a scientist, was far from self-evident. How then did the life of science become available and desirable, but only to some colonial subjects? My paper engages with recent anthropological accounts of the reproduction of caste privilege through scientific research and engineering education in contemporary India, through a historical case study of the upper caste uptake of technoscience in the early twentieth century. I will focus on the foundational years of a north Indian ‘experimental collective’ comprised by the readers, authors and editors of the Hindi science monthly *Vigyan* (1915) in Allahabad and examine how the life of science came to be a desired ideal amongst its male, high caste Hindu readership. I will draw out the cultural archetypes, scenes of familial nurture, and infrastructural conditions used to narrate life in science across the genres of biography, reportage and fiction in *Vigyan*. Attending to the foundational terms upon which the authority of modern scientific practitioners was rendered in this collective, I propose two concepts – interest and disposition – as contributions to a conceptual toolkit for addressing castelessness before and beyond “merit”. I argue that the Indian subject’s interest in and disposition for science is a critical site of caste’s modern rearrangement as technoscience.

Caste, Race and the History of Statistical Objectivity *Sayori Ghoshal*

Is caste in India simply an analogy of race in the West? Or do caste and race intersect in ways that significantly determine histories of marginalization of the non-Hindu Other in the subcontinent? Further, what is the history of the intersection of caste and race beyond the realm of identity politics? How was caste-race a significant category in producing the nationalist

discipline of statistics in early 20th c. India? In the early to mid-20th century, Indian anthropologists and statisticians traced the racial lineages of Dalits and Indian Muslims in order to ascertain origins. The studies show how despite rejecting certain racist claims (such as racial purity), modern Indian sciences perpetuated other assumptions, such as the relevance of studying race admixture in particular castes and the certainty that the degree of mixture could be measured precisely. Father of Indian statistics, Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis, in analyzing the racial roots of Anglo-Indians asked whether they were “more closely allied with the Hindus? or with the Mahomedans? Do they show a greater affinity with the higher castes of Bengal or with the lower castes?” (1927). In responding to such questions, Mahalanobis was able to devise his famous coefficient (D2) which was a measure of the degree of resemblance and distance between two populations. Based on such archival instances, my paper would analyze the epistemological role caste-race played in the anticolonial, nationalist history of statistical objectivity in India. In effect, I argue for the importance of bringing political history of identities in conversation with the histories of disciplinary knowledges.

Session Organizer:

Palashi Vaghela, Cornell University

Discussant:

Shivani Kapoor, O P Jindal Global University

309. Celebrating and Critiquing Feminist Inclusion Strategies in Technoscience Communities - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Science and technology communities come in many forms, from the elite community of research scientists within the academy to the myriad grassroots communities that spring up to take direct action on technology policy issues. Yet despite this wide variation in technoscience communities, many continue to reproduce gendered patterns of exclusion visible in science and technology more broadly. This panel provides space for critiquing community practices and structures of exclusion that contribute to limiting who can participate in the production of technoscientific knowledge, who can contribute to decision-making around policy and innovation priorities, and who gets to design the technological products and infrastructure that shape our lives. But, in line with this year’s theme of “good relations”, it also aims to celebrate successful inclusion strategies, to identify replicable practices for enhancing community diversity, and to highlight radical experiments in relationship-building and community development. We believe that this year, of all years, this celebration of progress is particularly important. We welcome contributions—from any geographical location in the Global South or North—that explore feminist community inclusion strategies from a wide range of theoretical approaches. These could include (but are not limited to): communities of practice; space and place-making; social field theory; identity theory; affect theory; participatory design and co-design practices; and critical making. We also welcome practice-oriented presentations that are not necessarily based in theory. We particularly welcome intersectional contributions that look at issues of gender inclusion/exclusion alongside axes of “race”, ethnicity, class, (dis)ability, transgender status, sexual identity, etc.

Participants:

A Different Archive: Honoring Cultural Memory in COVID-19 Research *Brooke Bosley, Georgia Institute of Technology; Brandy Pettijohn, Georgia Institute of Technology; Susana M. Morris, Georgia Institute of Technology*

COVID-19 vaccine distribution in the United States has been marked by unequal distribution and intense skepticism, especially from Black communities. The narrative used to explain vaccine hesitancy is the Tuskegee Experiment. The experiment is a well-known example of medical racism expansive traditional archives available, including texts, doctors’ records, photographs, and recordings marking the history. Our

paper argues that traditional approaches to understanding issues like vaccine hesitancy in Black communities in fields like STS or technoscience need a process rooted in cultural memory and archives. This paper presents Cultural Memory Archival Methodology (CMAM) grounded in archival work, cultural memory, and Black feminism in researching Black communities in social sciences. Cultural memory is the process of collective and personal experiences shaping the future. Archives are physical and digital locations that provide a sense of place and belonging. Applying CMAM as an epistemological approach allows us to use the archive as an anchor that either broadens the scope of cultural memory or uses it as a standpoint to create an archive. The paper uses CMAM in the case study of COVID-19 vaccines in Black communities with a digital archive that includes videos, transcriptions, photographs, medical documents of the medical histories of Black communities grounded in the work of feminist and STS scholars Cara Page, Alondra Nelson, Dorthey Roberts, and others. Our approach begins with the healing practices of Black people in the United States through midwifery, rootwork, and other alternative medicine practices. We believe CMAM offers a valuable epistemological process in STS.

For epistemic equity and the inclusion of women and vulnerable groups *Xenia Anaïd Rueda, UNAM*

This paper aims to analyze the theory of knowledge and the philosophy of science from a feminist perspective that questions the very nature of scientific knowledge and the power it creates to incorporate new perspectives towards a philosophy of science that blurs epistemic injustices that lie from its formation in the theory of knowledge. For this, in addition to the theoretical analysis, a case study will be included, carried out in a community in Mexico that shows that inclusion is possible through epistemic equity in which the knowledge that emerges from other systems of knowledge, different from scientific and technological. This case study will describe the process through which various concepts were integrated and put into practice, in which there was a production of knowledge among the various actors who intervened to promote social justice.

The definers of gendered innovations *Gita Ghiasi, Université de Montréal; Vincent Larivière, Université de Montréal; Tanja Tajmel, Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA)*

Gendered innovation is an approach put forward by Londa Schiebinger and reflects on the incorporation of gender and sex analysis into scientific and technological innovations. Several studies show that there is an association between the higher representation of women authors and papers that consider gender-related factors. However, an important question remains: what are the differences between the topics covered by women-led and men-led papers from different regions of the world? This study aims to reconstruct the definers of gender-related studies across disciplines and countries and to provide a better understanding of whose knowledge is mostly used to define the gender case of innovation. One proxy for the use of knowledge is citations, in the sense that citations received by a paper are indicators of its use and application in the creation of new knowledge. Accordingly, this study applies bibliometrics and focuses on those papers from Web of Science whose titles, abstracts and keywords incorporate gender-related keywords. Gender-related keyword filters are identified using the European Institute for Gender Equality (EIGE)'s Gender Equality Glossary and Thesaurus. Received citation data are further normalized by field and year of publication. This study contributes to the discourse on knowledge authority over gender-related science and aims to add to the conversation about the definers and describers of gender-related knowledge.

Session Organizers:

Em O'Sullivan, University College London

Isha Bhallamudi, University of California, Irvine

Patricia Pena, University of Chile, Institute of Image and Communication

310. Confronting Worlds: The Concept of "World" and its Stakes - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

The world is at stake. Pandemics, climate change, species extinctions, and toxic waste confront policy-makers, scientists, artists, activists, and citizens from around the planet. But what does it mean to be in a world? Are there many worlds or just one? And what kinds of worlds do we want to make? If worlds, as Donna Haraway writes, are not given so much as made, then what other worlds are possible? And how can they be brought into being? "Worlds" and "worlding" have emerged as productive theoretical and practical concepts in science studies as well as other fields. "World" is a seductive concept because of its expansiveness, drawing attention to the relationships between the global, the planetary, and the (other)worldly. Following Jakob Von Uexküll, "world" can make inroads into nonhuman or multispecies domains. "Worlding" inspires flights of imagination, as in the world-building stories of speculative fiction. "World" is helpful in thinking about incommensurabilities and alterities. Scholars have mobilized "world" to think of culture and context differently, as an alternative to fraught analytics such as the "global" or "scalability" and their imperial and universalizing ambitions. In this session, we invite presentations that critically reflect on the ordering concept of "world" and to consider new directions for investigating the world or worlds in science studies. What does this concept afford us? How might worlds serve epistemically, ontologically, or politically? What are the ethical stakes of worlds or worlding? We welcome traditional or multimodal presentations that explore these questions.

Participants:

Thinking Without "the World" *Laura A. Meek, University of Hong Kong*

This paper takes up the question of "the world" by attending to what kind of analytic, ontological, and grounding work this phrase does in anthropological writing. As a point of departure, I recount my dismay at learning that my close friend and housemate in Tanzania did not "know" that "the world" was round and her reciprocal dismay at my ignorance of the duality of being, of dimensions both seen and unseen. Approaching this encounter as 'doing difference together' (Verran 2013), I ask what was at stake for each of us in considering these characteristics as defining features of "the world". Many anthropologists today approach such questions ontologically, considering how worlds—in the plural—are enacted through practices and composed via assemblages, rather than given a priori (de la Cadena 2015, Langwick 2011, West 2007). Meanwhile, critics of this approach accuse the ontological turn of an exoticism that implies different people exist in different worlds altogether (Graeber 2015, Doostdar 2018). In this paper, I think through the use of the term "world" by scholars on both sides of this debate, asking: What work does this term do? Does it impose connection or containment as a framing device? What temporal and spatial orientations might it presuppose, even when used in the plural? I conclude, ala Wittgenstein, by acknowledging that the "world-picture" is "Above all...the substratum of all my enquiring and asserting", too (1969: 23e).

Decolonizing hope: Imagining pluriversal alternatives, one world at a time *Saurabh Arora, University of Sussex; Cian O'Donovan, University College London*

How are collective struggles for sustainability and racial justice, underpinned by hope for other worlds on earth? How do these hopes go beyond coloniality that lies at the heart of Modernity and its variants in postcolonial societies, which are associated with climate catastrophes, losses of species and languages, and now a pandemic exacerbating inequalities? – In mainstream discussions on sustainability and justice, hope for another world is colonized by socio-material change driven by 'eco-modernist

technofixes' or the rhetoric of 'green and inclusive capitalism'. This drive leaves unchallenged forms of ongoing coloniality that superiorise Modern worlds using categorisations of race, rationality, civilization, nationality, caste, and religion. Often it also fails to confront extractivism based on objectification of nonhuman beings and processes in 'nature'. Contrasting hopes for other worlds go beyond climate and environmental justice for victims of Modernisation. Justice that is grounded in survivors' quests to thrive in egalitarian coexistence. Hopes for other worlds are pluriversal, geared towards realising a world in which 'many worlds fit'. In this paper, we attempt to mat rather than map, hopes for other worlds through multimedia archival work with movements for sustainability and decolonial justice. We find that imaginations of pluriversal alternatives past and future, foreground four connected horizons for decolonizing hope. They include transforming ways of relating: a) Beyond Nation, through communality and intercultural conviviality; b) Beyond Human, through multiplying human-nature relations of radical care; c) Beyond Science, through epistemic justice and handcrafting futures; and d) Beyond Time, through cosmologies of divergent becoming of worlds.

Slime-Worlds. Reconstructing the Global with Physarum Polycephalum *Maria Debinska, Institute of Archaeology and Ethnology, Polish Academy of Sciences*

This presentation regards interdisciplinary practices that use the slime mold *Physarum polycephalum* as a research tool for reconstructing and optimizing human transportation networks. It aims to depict and analyze the image of the world that emerges in the interactions between humans and slime mold in the lab. Slime molds are some of the oldest terrestrial organisms, which combine the characteristics of fungi and animals; in the biological taxonomy they are classified as Protists. *Physarum polycephalum* is one of the most intensely researched slime molds. It is easy to culture in the lab and it forms a network of protein tubes between its food sources (in lab conditions – usually oat flakes), finding the shortest paths; for this quality it has been used in computer programming and communication systems modeling. Famously, *Physarum polycephalum* has been employed to reconstruct and optimize human transportation networks (Tero et al. 2010; Adamatzky 2012). In my presentation I will enquire what notions of the world and the global have been re-produced in this process. First, I will describe the worlding practices that occur at the intersection of the human and the slimy to demonstrate that the relationship between the slimy and the abstract, the world and its model, is an unstable opposition always ready to be upended. Then, I will reconstruct the image of the world that emerges from those practices as well as the underlying images of the end of the world to argue, that the world is an always already apocalyptic concept.

“Here be Dragons:” Inquiry Beyond “World’s” End *Jonathan Wald, McGill University*

How does one ethically conduct inquiry when the world seems to be falling apart? Is a turn towards broader conceptualizations of “worlding” the necessary response for this moment? Drawing on fieldwork with environmental scientists addressing climate change in Minas Gerais, Brazil in the leadup to Jair Bolsonaro’s election, this presentation interrogates the utility of the concept of “world” as a means to diagnose the multifaceted horrors of the climate crisis. Taking inspiration from the dragons which marked the limits of knowledge in medieval atlases as well as the monstrous Titan which gave the atlas its name, I suggest that analytical emphasis on “world,” “worlding,” and “worldhood” may encourage observers to prioritize elements of composition, harmony, and structure, potentially overlooking productive capacities of breakdown, mutation, and alienation. Following Enrique Dussel’s philosophy of liberation, the titanic scope of the concept of “world” risks reproducing the colonial orderings of beings which exist beyond the framings of Eurocentric understanding. To present a concrete challenge to this worlding

project, I turn to examples of inquiry faced with monstrous enmity, such as the study of Yellow Fever-infected mosquitoes which emerged in the aftermath of a toxic flood, as instances of inquiry which set aside the totalizing aspirations of the “world” concept. Crucially, these examples of inquiry demonstrate that the end of the “world” concept is not necessarily a moment to be feared.

Session Organizers:

Jonathan Wald, McGill University
Darcie A DeAngelo, University of Oklahoma
Fiona Gedeon Achi

Chair:

Julianne Yip, Mitacs

311. Transforming the Development & Governance of Pharmaceuticals - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Major changes are underway within the pharmaceutical sector that are associated with shifts in research, innovation and business models from blockbuster products intended for large patient populations to more niche products designed for smaller, more targeted populations. Innovation is underway in how drugs are being researched and developed, and how they are being manufactured, used, evaluated, licensed and paid for. While some of these changes are tied to genomics and the rise of personalized medicine, others result of patient activism and disease politics. These technical and political developments put pressure on public regulators and payers, resulting in novel forms of governance, including the use of real world data and conditional reimbursement. This panel builds on STS scholarship on the socio-technical production of pharmaceutical knowledge, as well as its material and biopolitical impacts. We invite papers from a range of international perspectives that critically analyze these transformations, as well as those that highlight forms of alternative pharmaceutical practices and methods that are more sustainable and offer more just and equitable access to treatments. Topics may include but are not limited to: – Forms of open pharmaceutical innovation – Industry dynamics and changing business models – Patient groups and new forms of knowledge production – R&D partnerships across public, not-for-profit and/or private sector – Drug repurposing and off-label use – Changing regulatory knowledge and forms of evaluation – Pharmaceutical pricing and access – Novel access arrangement and alternative regulatory frameworks for coverage – Future health care system sustainability and social solidarity.

Participants:

In-House Hospital Manufacturing Of CAR-T Cells In Canada As A Emerging Form Of “Social Pharmaceutical Innovation” *Conor Douglas, York Univeristy; Faisal Ali Mohamed, York University, Toronto*

CAR-T cell treatments demonstrate the potential to be an effective treatment option for cancer patients. This therapy does not require traditional chemotherapy, which has harsh side effects for patients. CAR-T therapy also shows promising results in patients by keeping cancer in remission longer. Despite this, there are challenges facing this type of treatment. Manufacturing of CAR-T cells is more complex as the approach requires a single batch to be tailored for an individual patient. Without economies of scale, the cost of such a treatment remains high. The high price of CAR-T treatment has also been a tough pill to swallow for public and private insurers. BioCanRx is a Canadian network of public and private stakeholders working together to develop and manufacture cancer immunotherapies. In February 2017, BioCanRx announced a plan to manufacture CAR-T cells in Canada, and is funding a clinical trial (CLIC-1901) which uses CAR-T cells in patients with relapsed and refractory CD-19 positive hematologic malignancies. This trial can be viewed as an example of “social pharmaceutical innovation” through alternative forms of both provisioning and licensing. The in-house hospital manufacturing of CAR-T cells can address some current logistical challenges of CAR-T treatments. These R&D

partnerships involve multiple stakeholders and funders including the Canadian federal government, provincial governments, the BC Cancer Foundation and the University of Ottawa who are all involved in the advancement of this pioneering study. We believe these types of “social pharmaceutical innovation” are crucial for addressing the treatment challenges, particularly for patients with rare diseases.

Moral Innovation without Market Incentives: The (Im)possibilities of Pediatric Drug Development Under Current Pharmaceutical Models *Kasia Tolwinski, McGill University; Margaret Chiappetta, York University*

Pediatric brain tumors (PBT) are the leading cause of cancer-related death in children under the age of 20. Standard treatments are often ineffective and have significant effects on quality of life. New “precision medicine” treatments using genomic and molecular analyses have a great deal of potential, but there seem to be barriers in bringing targeted treatments to pediatric populations. Rare diseases like PBT affect small numbers of children; stakeholders in research and industry argue that there is no incentive to for industry to invest money to in developing drugs for such small markets. Through participant observation in workshops and conferences and in-depth interviews with 70 stakeholders, we map the moral, technical, and social ecosystem of pediatric brain tumor research and treatment, revealing a complex and layered system of barriers and opportunities. In this paper, we first discuss how the current pipeline model of drug innovation does not account for relational complexity and communication flows, and by extension, cannot address failures. We then show how a small group of industry stakeholders are attempting to remedy the problems of a lack of incentives and small markets by appealing to a moral obligation to children’s health that exceeds a for-profit framework. Their experience is evidence that financial and technological fixes are insufficient to address social and ethical quandaries at the heart of medicine, ultimately revealing the complexity of furthering innovation and care.

Stalinist Citizen Science: Grassroots Drug Development in the Early Cold War USSR *Pavel Vasilyev, HSE University St. Petersburg*

Citizen science has been mostly studied in Western contexts and, more recently, also in some indigenous and Global South settings (e.g., by Cori Hayden, Inkeri Koskinen, Hagit Keysar). This article takes a different perspective and addresses the topic in the unlikely context of a state socialist country. Drawing on pioneering work by Ekaterina Rybkina and Elena Aronova, this paper asks what forms citizen science could take in the USSR and inquires more specifically into the politics of grassroots drug development in the late 1940s and early 1950s. Having to deal with the catastrophic legacy of the Nazi invasion and facing a new wave of isolationism with the emerging Cold War, the Soviets consciously sought to involve ordinary citizens in the process of scientific discovery through the programs of ‘inventiveness’ (izobretatel’stvo) and ‘efficiency drive’ (ratsionalizatorstvo). Accordingly, in this paper, I draw on the archival collections of the Soviet Ministry of Health at the State Archive of the Russian Federation and examine the correspondence between local innovators on the ground and the central drug regulator in Moscow, the Pharmacological Committee. In doing so, I show how the emerging autarkic and nationalist rhetoric of the early Cold War was creatively employed by Soviet citizen scientists to advance their initiatives and even to claim certain epistemic supremacy over established forms of biomedical knowledge. The paper also considers the broader implications of this case study for socialist politics of innovation, grassroots scientific activism, and the processes of drug discovery and testing in the contemporary world.

Causing headwinds? How Dutch actors conceive situated futures for magistral preparation of pharmaceuticals *Tineke*

Kleinhou-Vliek, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University; Marlous Arentshorst, Copernicus Institute for Sustainable Development, Utrecht University; Wouter Boon, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University; Jarno Hoekman; Rob Hagendijk, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research, University of Amsterdam; Shona Kalkman, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University; Ellen Moors, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University

Background: High prices of drugs for rare diseases regularly threaten their accessibility. Magistral preparation, i.e., the production of medicines in a pharmacy, is an alternative way of producing drugs that may help address this problem. In the Netherlands, there has been a lack of clarity surrounding the use of this relatively controversial method. We ask: how do concerned actors construct situated futures (that is, envisioned, legitimated in-use situations) for magistral preparation? And how have these changed from 2017 to 2021, during which magistral preparation became more institutionalised? Methods: We held three focus groups in 2017 with patients, doctors, and payers (totalling n=21 respondents) and interviews with pharmacists (n=8). We repeated these in 2021 in four focus groups in digital format (n=25). Results: In 2017, respondents saw the potential for magistral preparation in specific circumstances, such as temporary unavailability of medicines or necessary dose optimisation for children, but also when pharmaceutical producers had crossed a moral line. For example, if innovative work had not preceded a drug’s (steep) price increase. In 2021, reflecting on how recently formal advice to the government has endorsed magistral preparation in precisely such a situation, our respondents were excited about this potentiality. Conclusion: Concerned actors consider the use of magistral preparation legitimated in specific circumstances, a.o. to cause headwinds for the pharmaceutical industry when they are considered morally in the wrong. The situated futures they conceive of thus have distinctly moral dimensions. The substantive robustness of these value-rich situated futures provides an avenue for future research.

Session Organizers:

Conor Douglas, York University

Paul Martin, Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield

Tineke Kleinhou-Vliek, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University

Chair:

Paul Martin, Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield

312. **Craft, Computers, and Conquest: Renegotiating relations - II**

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Situated Computations is an approach to design and computation that grounds technologies in the social world by acknowledging the historical, cultural, and material contexts of designing and making. It acknowledges and responds to a setting’s social and technological infrastructures, and refuses to remain ignorant of economic and political structures that shape it (Noel 2020). In conversation with the conference theme, we invite scholarship that reflects on manual and digital practices to reveal ways in which existing and new oppressions in these sites are maintained or challenged. Our purpose is to examine manual and technological practices inside and outside academia through STS lenses of feminism, post-colonialism, and justice. We ask: How might analog and digital methods contribute to, destroy, or bridge long standing oppressions and strategic sortings of society? How might we conceptualize “good” relations in these practices to frame and enact new relations that confront colonialism, racism, and inequality? We invite works that explore theories, methods and

expressions around craft, justice, and technology. How might praxis in situated computations help us identify and reclaim marginalized spaces? What new academic spaces might we reimagine to renegotiate and challenge power relations between those “inside” and those “outside” academia? What links may we draw between the lived experiences of craftspersons and the design of technological systems? Our goal is to imagine how praxis between craft and technological systems can be a source of theoretical and methodological interventions that can attend to racism, inequality and other oppressions in technoscience.

Participants:

Wire-bending: Not just a craft, but a kind of carnival *Vernelle A Noel, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Carnival theory is usually based on the work of Bakhtin who characterizes carnival by a temporary suspension of hierarchy of society and individuals, with all participants being considered equal. Performance theorist, Richard Schechner, offers a theoretical redefinition of carnival that focuses on the values and sense of community that it affirms and proposes five key aspects of this new theory describing the Trinidad Carnival. In this paper, I place three concepts from this Schechner’s theory adjacent to empirical studies of wire-bending in the Carnival to give new insight into the relationship between wire-bending, carnival, and socio-cultural aspects of Trinbagonian life. The three concepts I extend are: (1) differences rubbing up against each other; (2) unity and tension as seeds of creativity; and (3) creative tensions between constraint and freedom. This theorizing exists at the intersection of the traditional and the technological, the social, corporeal, and material. Based on these theoretical encounters, I suggest that wire-bending is not just a craft, but a microcosm of carnival, a kind of carnival. This reconceptualization contributes to theoretical descriptions of wire-bending, extends the practice beyond Carnival, and facilitates the application of wire-bending as a theory for design, education, and practice.

Building the Black Box – reflexive digital practices in archaeology and beyond *Mike Kelly, UNIVERSITY OF BRIGHTON*

In the theoretical literature of archaeological research, the ideals of reflexive and self-critical practice are well established. In practice however, cultural heritage research tools and knowledge representation techniques often fail to adequately reflect the nuanced philosophical positions of research theory, and instead tend to reflect the concerns of a positivist outlook. Drucker (2014) argues that in their formal emphases on objectivity and universality, conventional representation techniques tend to marginalise uncertainty and the subjective experience and influence of the researcher. From its place in the border territories of science and the humanities, archaeology has at times struggled to reconcile interpretation with the scientific method. In the domain of computer-aided archaeological reconstructions, for example, attempts have been made to formalise the representation of uncertainty and the sharing of process, or ‘paradata’. In my research I argue that such initiatives do not necessarily incorporate the epistemological shift required to integrate the full implications of uncertainty and subjectivity in knowledge construction. What are the metaphors we use to design our software tools, and is it time they were updated? Based on Latour’s (1987) strategy of studying science in the making, rather than the ‘black box’ of ready-made science, I discuss my PhD research into the use of digital tools and the web for reflexive practice and knowledge making. I explore the potential of electronic research journals and open publishing models for reducing the opacity of assumed truths and inviting the reimagining of research outputs. This is a theoretical paper from a mid-PhD research project.

Losing Grip: Reorienting situated practice with automated technologies *James Forren, Dalhousie University; Claire Nicholas, University of Oklahoma*

This paper considers automated technologies not as a disruption

of a pristine mind-body-material system, but as re-orientating devices within an already messy, provisional network of mind, body, tools, and matter. Anthropological studies of contemporary design already identify continual commingling of physical and mental labours through gesture, speech, silence, and shared attention in, around, and through both digital and analogue tools and materials (Loukissas, Yaneva, Murphy, Nicholas / Oak, Turkle). Read through a feminist lens, automated technologies in this milieu may unsettle, transform or perpetuate existing power dynamics and dominant knowledges by providing new objects of attention and desire, new affordances, and new terms of access. Rather than gripping more tightly to an imagined mind-body-material system that never was, this paper seeks ways to navigate our experience of losing grip on tools and materials. This paper shares transdisciplinary design anthropology research using audio and video recordings, process portfolios, and fieldnotes within a computational design investigation. The authors – a researcher in computational design and making, and a researcher in anthropology and material culture studies – seek to understand if feminist modalities of auto-and collaborative ethnography (Ellis, Lassiter, Behar), analyzed through ecological (Ingold, Hodder), feminist (Haraway, Wajcman), and queer (Ahmed) lenses can adaptively reorient creative process with automated technologies. Might recording how we perceive matter (and the intentionality of instruments we see it through) aide us in drawing nearer to that matter as it appears to slip away?

Session Organizer:

Vernelle A Noel, Georgia Institute of Technology

Discussant:

Hayri Dortdivanlioglu, Georgia Institute of Technology

313. Data-Based Biomedicine: Legacies, Frictions, Ontologies II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Biomedicine increasingly relies upon the production, gathering, curation, organization, and sharing of large volumes of data through databases (Chow-White and Garcia-Sancho, 2012). Building upon social studies of computing and biomedicine, this panel investigates data-based biomedicine as it emerges from situated practices of scientific activity. It addresses, but is not limited to, three sets of interrelated questions: First, what are the socio-historical drivers of these ‘database-ization’ processes? While links between computer and biomedical sciences – particularly in relation to genomics – have been usefully sketched out (Garcia-Sancho, 2011), much remains to be done regarding how biomedical data ‘got its bases’ (Haigh, 2009). Second, how does data-based biomedicine effectively assemble technological (algorithms, chips, software) and organizational (consortia, standards, benchmarks) configurations, and how is this new ‘style of practice’ (Keating and Cambrosio, 2012) stabilized in a diversity of domains of biomedicine (e.g. cancer, infectious diseases, public health)? Third, how are data of biological (e.g. ‘omics’ data), biographical and/or social processes (e.g. social capital, social belongings, patient-reported outcomes, scores of psychosocial complexity) assembled into data-based understandings of health and illness? Making data visible and reliable to as many practitioners as possible entails an increasing work to produce, relate, and standardize biomedical and socio-epidemiological data (Bossen et al., 2019). Through what inclusions/exclusions are bio-social ontologies of health emerging from the intelligibility and interoperability of these data? In parallel to historical focus on path dependencies, the panel invites empirical and conceptual socio-anthropological contributions highlighting the disruptive alignments and frictions (Edwards et al., 2011) that shape data-based biomedicine.

Participants:

On Entanglements And Separations Of Sample/Data Along Their Journey Through Biobanks *Ingrid Metzler, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies; Lisa-Maria Ferent; Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies*

Biobanks are often described as collections of samples (or

biomaterials) and associated data. Yet, it remains unspecified what the “and” between samples and data means in practice as well as what the notion of “associated” stands for. This paper explores the relations between samples and data in the context of hospital-based biobanks. Methodologically, we draw on materials collected in five hospital-based biobanks in Austria between 2019 and 2021, which include interviews, observations, and documents. We approach biobanks as assemblages and use the lens of “sample/data voyages” in our analysis. We unpack and compare moments in which samples and data are produced and (dis)entangled, including moments in which sample/data are made amenable to travel, are (re)used or destroyed. The comparison of similarities and differences of such moments helps us, first, to explore variations in the meaning of the slash between sample and (various kinds of) data. Second, it also allows us to distill ways in which responsibilities for taking care of sample/data are distributed and/or shared in hospital-based biobanking. Specifically, it sheds light on the different ways in which the “doable” and the “desirable” shape the situated practices underpinning sample/data voyages in hospital biobanks, and to foreground the values and affects involved in biobanking.

Producing Dis/order: Assembling Autism in Big Data Biobanking *Kathryne Metcalf, University of California San Diego*

This project traces an ecology of biobanks within autism research, situating the work of data production, maintenance, distribution, and reuse as a central process. I explore how biobank data travels through scientific research and serves to organize the relationship between genotypic origins and phenotypic outcomes by analyzing the last decade of academic literature using data from two large biobanks. The first, 23andMe, is a direct-to-consumer recreational genetic testing company whose health metrics are self-reported. In contrast, MSSNG—a partnership between parental advocacy organization Autism Speaks and Verily (formerly Google Life Sciences)—circulates whole-genome data representing families rather than individuals, produced through clinical observation and management. The “data journeys” (Leonelli 2016) that these data undertake materially shape their contents, and frequently involve recombination with data from other institutional actors. I map these journeys alongside the theoretical, methodological, and discursive apparatuses employed by the researchers who analyze them. The resulting network charts a provocative series of epistemic and ontological disjunctures regarding what autism is and how it can be understood through genomic investigation. Reading these findings through the histories of MSSNG and 23andMe within the longer trajectory of American autism research, I argue that these and other biobanks have created the conditions of possibility for evolving regimes of disciplinary legitimacy and biomedical authority in the construction of geneticized social dis/order.

Species, communities and the meaning of the genome *Miguel García-Sancho, University of Edinburgh; James W. E. Lowe, Science, Technology and Innovation Studies, University of Edinburgh*

In this paper, we argue that the relationship of a reference DNA sequence with the communities that produced and use the sequence data profoundly shapes the perceived potential of that data as a genomic representation. We show this by examining three international projects that finalised the first whole-genome reference sequences of yeast, human and pig between 1996 and 2011. While a majority of the laboratories determining the yeast genome also used the sequence data to study the biology of this organism, the human reference sequence was produced by large-scale genome centres that were distinct from the communities of human and medical geneticists. The pig reference genome was also primarily determined at large-scale centres, but in close collaboration with animal geneticists. The yeast genome

represented only one specific strain: S288C of *S. cerevisiae*, that had previously been adopted by life scientists from different fields as a model organism. The Human Genome Project presumed its reference sequence to be an abstract representation of humans in their diversity. By contrast, the pig genetics community’s awareness of the limits of the representational scope of the reference sequence encouraged the development of versions appropriate to distinct breeds and requirements. The different ways in which the representativeness of reference sequences was constructed and construed suggests that the ‘translational gap’ that post-genomic research endeavours to bridge may be an artifactual generalisation: it fails to capture the distinct historicities of genomics in non-human species, where the distance between the sequence and user communities is not as pronounced.

Session Organizers:

Nolwenn Bühler, STS Lab, University of Lausanne

Nils Graber, STS Lab, University of Lausanne

Florian Jatton, STS Lab, University of Lausanne

Francesco Panese, University of Lausanne, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences

Discussant:

Luca Chiapperino, University of Lausanne

314. Diseased Landscapes: Health and Illness in Territories of Extraction - IV - RESISTANCE

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Through the theme of Diseased Landscapes, this panel explores how the nexus of extractivism and political conflict affects environmental and human health. It aims at bringing together efforts in scholarly practice—including art-based methodologies and activist-oriented research—to historically, politically, and socially situate disease, toxins, pathogens, non-humans, and bodily dysfunction in violent geographies produced by legal and illegal extractivism. We ask how the health conditions of the environment and the body become entangled in places dominated by extractivist economies. What difference does it make to tell stories of armed violence, gendered and racialized dispossession, capitalism, mining, and agrarian expansion through human and more-than-human experiences of health and illness? How are evidence and ignorance about bodies and landscapes produced, used, and abused in contexts marked by extractivist activities? And finally, what practices, methods, and interventions are helpful to establish good relations, capable of disrupting the combined production of disease and violence in old, new, and future territories of extraction?

Participants:

Doing undone science: counter-expertise and resistances to uranium mining in Caetité/Bahia/Brasil *Bruno Lucas Saliba de Paula*

This research project aims to analyze, through the conceptual framework from the field of Science and Technology Studies (STS), public engagement and resistances of people from Caetité/Bahia in front of the uranium mining and processing made by Indústrias Nucleares do Brasil (INB). Since it started in 1999, the extraction of uranium has been subject of intense debates. It would be associated with an abnormal incidence of cancer among local population and also with possible environmental contaminations. We seek to analyze the constitution of two regimes of knowledge and practices that permeate these issues. On the one hand, the official scientific perspective, present mainly in the positions of INB’s technical staff and in inspection institutions. On the other hand, the knowledge and practices produced by “lay people”, workers and residents of the region affected by uranium mining, as well as the alternative researches and data produced by them in alliance with independent scientists. Our preliminary results indicate that INB technocratically reiterates the natural of the presence of uranium in the environment, taking no responsibility for it. In contrast,

social movements indicate a direct relationship between uranium mining, contamination and the cases of cancer. Thus, we perceive “counter-expertise” initiatives mobilized by activists, which would produce new evidences and stimulate debates on neglected issues, filling in the absences left by “undone science”.

Extracting Ayahuasca, Crafting Settings for Health under Brazilian Settler Colonialism *Emilia Sanabria, CNRS - CERMES3*

This paper asks how space can be held for healing within the diseased landscapes of colonialism. What does it mean to heal individuals when the territories in which they dwell – and from which they nourish themselves – are violently extracted, saturated in toxicity and inhospitable to regenerative forms of sociality? Drawing on ethnographic work on ayahuasca ritual practices circulating within Brazil (Acre, Bahia, Sao Paulo) and between Brazil and Europe, the paper explores and expands the idiom of “holding space” for ceremonial healing work in relation to the territorial dimensions of colonial and racial violence. I attend to the prosaic logistical challenges faced by what I tentatively call “ayahuasca ceremonial infrastructures” to carve out healing spaces within neocolonial territorial orders. STS work on the placebo, pharmaceuticals, and drugs (in particular psychedelics), analyses the intra-actions between substances and their “settings” in producing efficacies. This paper explores lines of flight between “setting” and “settler” colonial projects by attending to the ways settler colonial settings are, to a greater or lesser degree, contested or countered by ayahuasca ceremonial infrastructures. This will allow me to examine different ayahuasca ceremonial formations from the perspective of how they resist colonialisms and to ask about the durability of the counter-settings they manifest. As the global demand for ayahuasca booms, one way to track this is to examine how tightly or loosely the assemblage of community-territory-plants is held and how, as it is expanded, new ways of maintaining good relations, beyond the human, are imagined and realized.

Medical Enclosure, Ontological Openings: “Transversalizing” Mapuche Health and Human-Land Relations in Wallmapu/Southern Chile *Randall C Burson, Department of Anthropology, The University of Pennsylvania*

Within long-standing conflicts between the Chilean state and Mapuche nation, the Chilean government created an intercultural health system that simultaneously provides biomedical and indigenous treatment. However, these intercultural clinics are situated spatially and organizationally in a context where militarized police clash with Mapuche communities trying to reclaim ancestral territory from multinational forestry companies. In this entangled context, how are the relations between people and territory, and the boundaries between health and “not health” negotiated? To address this question, I draw on interviews and participant observations with biomedical and Mapuche practitioners, and intercultural health facilitators. First, I analyze how biomedical practice in Southern Chile’s intercultural clinics operationalizes a logic of “enclosure” that partitions and distances patients’ concerns from their context through biomedical techniques of referral and escalation. I argue that this process of enclosing patients’ concerns within biomedicine echoes colonial policies of land enclosure, which privatized and commodified the dispossessed Mapuche territory on which present-day forestry plantations and clinics are built. Next, following my interlocutors’ calls to “transversalize” health research, I discuss how my Mapuche interlocutors create and navigate “ontological openings” (de la Cadena 2014) to challenge the epistemic and institutional boundaries that dissociate illness from its socio-ecological context. This paper goes beyond elucidating the connections between disease, state violence, and extractive economies in Southern Chile to understand how these connections are made (il)legible through logics of enclosure and opening. Finally, it points us to “transversal” approaches to

healing as a means to work across healthcare, land management, and indigenous self-determination.

‘That Is the Price You Pay’: Local Rationality of Muscovites Concerning Health-Related Behavior and Environmental Risks *Daria Lebedeva, HSE University Moscow*

Over the past decades, the problem of environmental health has gained significant attention in public discussions. Particularly, some health risks associated with environmental factors can be reduced by individuals at the level of everyday behavioral practices, which is actively embedded in the public discourse. Individual’s self-care lifestyle is promoted in the rhetoric of the responsible and conscious citizen. However, according to the studies, among Russians there is limited reflexivity and proactivity towards environmental health. It is publicly framed as irrationality and irresponsibility of citizens in relation to their health and the environment, despite the pronounced extractivist framework of ‘society-environment’ relationship. Based on the data of in-depth interviews with Muscovites, the given research focuses on the lay theories applied to the relationship between health and environment, and aims to show that in the Russian context, the lack of concern about environmental health risks should be considered not as ignorance or illiteracy but as a deliberate strategy, local rationality of individuals in the setting of unresolved systemic basis for proactive selfcare and extractive economic institutions. We suggest that individuals evaluate costs and benefits of engaging in personal health-preserving and environmental practices – primarily, efforts and sacrifices needed versus benefits of economic growth and urbanization, time frame the likelihood – and make the argued decision to de-problematize environmental health risks. It constitutes an interesting case, and the issue of the balance between human society, natural environment, and technologies in the context of extractivist and industrial societies requires further STS research and public interventions.

Session Organizer:

Diana Ojeda, Universidad de los Andes, Bogotá, Colombia

Chair:

Ann Kelly, King's College London

Discussant:

Lina Beatriz Pinto-García, Universidad de los Andes

315. Conspiracy Theorists and Techno-Science - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

Techno-science, and the changes wrought by techno-science, frequently result in pushback. While such resistance can be grounded in attention to risks and social justice issues, this resistance can also take the form of conspiratorial reactions. From climate change denial to anti-vaccine movements, from fears of 5G towers to UFOs, from pseudoscience to conspiracy theories—instead of settling contentious debates, the creation of techno-scientific evidence has repeatedly led to conflict over what it is that particular evidence truly shows. Not simply consisting of a rejection of techno-science, conspiracy adherents marshal government documents and scientific reports in order to push for conclusions other than those found in those materials; with many conspiracy advocates learning to skillfully deploy the language of expertise in order to bolster, and spread, their claims. This session engages with the conference theme of “good relations” by approaching the matter of relations from the opposite direction. We seek to investigate the sorts of “bad,” “inappropriate,” “conspiratorial,” or “unforeseen” relations that emerge from modes of techno-scientific expertise and knowledge making. In what ways does the same evidence get mobilized by groups with differing agendas to advance bizarre claims? How have different media technologies afforded the efficient spread of such thinking? Beyond treating them as a source purely for concern or derision, what can (or should) STS scholars learn from studying pseudoscience and conspiracy theories? Beyond an assemblage of case studies, we hope our panel will demonstrate how views that are often treated as unserious deserve serious critical attention.

Participants:

Anti-Maskers, White Supremacy, and Transmisogyny *Juno Salazar Parrenas, Cornell University, Department of S&TS*

Slime molds with 720 sexes, spider monkeys with large clitorises mistaken by human observers to be penises, gynandromorphic song birds, and tulips having an option for asexual reproduction—these examples all point to the myriad ways in which what is understood as “biological” is materially queer, intersexed, and trans. Yet, US-based right wing conspiracy theorists regularly deploy the idea of biological sciences in their anti-trans attacks. For instance, QAnon-following US congresswoman Marjorie Taylor Green was parodied for having posted an anti-trans sign ‘trust the science’ when her beliefs about pandemics and forest fires are wildly unscientific. Her beliefs are unfortunately not isolated. This paper explores instances in which white supremacy converged with transmisogyny in contemporary right wing activism over 2020 mask mandates.

(Conspiracy) Theorizing the Outside *Annika Tara Nilsson, Washington University in St. Louis*

Contemporary conspiracy theorizing is highly attuned to the body and its boundaries, dysfunctions, and ailments; unexplained illnesses, genetic modification, bioweapons, and mysterious toxins loom large in the conspiratorial imagination. Mainstream critique of such theories, which cast aspersions on the culturally authoritative institution of biomedicine, tends to attribute them either to lack of “science literacy” or to hegemonic corporate manipulation. This paper proposes instead that conspiracy theorizing coheres around points of contact with the limitations of the dominant paradigm of knowledge production. Drawing from ongoing ethnographic fieldwork examining everyday knowledge production practices in a community of people whose experiences of living with medically unexplained illnesses have led them to reject biomedicine in favor of conspiratorially-inclined alternative epistemologies of health, illness, and the body, I suggest that conspiracy theorizing flourishes at those sites where culturally authoritative structures of knowledge push against their constitutive outsiders. Conspiracy theorizing might thus be productively conceived of as an attempt to find the terms with which to think that which is unthinkable from within the dominant paradigm of knowledge production. Attending closely to the epistemic structures of conspiracy theorizing may enable us to more clearly perceive the contours of the present episteme and perhaps begin to develop new concepts with which to remake it. This paper will begin to put this into practice by examining the relation between the limits of evidence-based biomedicine’s ability to think difficult-to-quantify forms of embodied distress, such as pain and fatigue, with conspiratorial attempts to explain those conditions of illegibility.

“COVID-19 ‘Vaccine’ is a Literal Intracellular Hijacking Nanotechnology Virus”, and Other COVID-19 Conspiracy Theories *Anthony Trygub, Queens University*

COVID-19 conspiracy theories have proliferated since the beginning of the pandemic, to the extent that some scholars have characterized it as an ‘infodemic.’ This paper presents findings from a qualitative analysis of COVID-19 conspiracy theories on the Reddit forum of r/conspiracy, collected from March-August 2020. Conspiracy theories about COVID-19 are wide-ranging, but significant strands centre around the pandemic as a conspiracy of the wealthy elite, with vaccines seen as a eugenic technology deployed by the ‘deep state’ for purposes of population control. Drawing on anti-essentialist approaches which understand anti-science conspiracy theories not as the outcome of deficient knowledge but as driven by social problems, I argue that the thread running through these conspiracy theories is a theme of class struggle. Conspiracy theorists fear that wealthy elites are exploiting the pandemic for their own economic benefit at the expense of the working class

people’s lives and freedoms. They articulate feelings of losing control of their everyday lives, disillusionment and betrayal by the government and institutional systems which are meant to assist them. They also routinely make reference to perceived historical injustices, most clearly expressed in references to the 2008 financial crisis and post-9/11 surveillance legislation. Thus, although these conspiracy theories are mistaken about the causalities they construct, we can still learn a great deal from them about the feelings, social problems, and belief systems which drives them. I conclude that developing a better understanding of Coronavirus conspiracy theories may ultimately also help improving public health communication.

Reason and Conspiracy Theory in Contemporary Vaccine Hesitancy *Marco Delloca, UC Davis*

This essay reflects on two aspects of vaccine hesitancy. Accepting the invitation that animates this conference, I want to ask: what would it mean to entertain good relations with antivaxxers? To do so, I first examine the connection between antivaxxer epistemologies and the thought habit we have come to know as “conspiracy theory”: more and more removed from “mainstream” modes of thought exchange and circulation of information, antivaxxer thinkers form their public in conversation with “fringe” epistemologies that value different kinds of evidence, based on a complex array of uncanny connections: emotions and relatability are put in conversation with data and statistics; the posture of “revelation” we have learnt to associate to scientific discoveries comes to be paralleled in the purported disclosure of evil associations between policy makers and industry, between bio-science and capitalism. To what extent does this characterization approximate vaccine hesitancy to conspiracy theory? What is gained and lost through this approximation? Secondly, I want to imagine modes of recomposition: What use do antivaxxer thinkers find in science, and conversely of what use could antivaxxer thinkers be, in order to speculate a different one? By drawing partial connections between scholars that have accounted for other genres of science denial, and the work of Paul Feyerabend, I want to speculate on what ways of “doing science otherwise” (Stengers, 2017) could open from a generative relation between modern immunology and the concerns of vaccine hesitant thinkers.

Session Organizers:

Zachary M Loeb, History & Sociology of Science, University of Pennsylvania

Kate Dorsch, The University of Pennsylvania

316. **Becoming with Water: Ethnographic and Methodological Reconfigurations — IV**

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

This panel draws attention to the multiscalar, mutable, and unpredictable entanglements of water and the more than human amidst human intentions to control the environment. The authors' attention to complex ecological formations/assemblages attune us to the sensorium of knowing that encapsulate scientific and engineering techniques while also extending beyond it. Highlighting the confluence of global and local flows as contingent on the movement of water, the papers theoretically and methodologically demand attention to nonhuman multispecies affectations. Life forms becoming with water therefore calls for STS to engage not only to the part that nonhuman entities play in these technoscientific interactions, but rather, how these different life(s) intertwine by following the transformations that emerge in multispecies encounters across temporalities, spatialities, modalities.

Participants:

Valoration of Changes in Fishing Activity Associated with Water Quality in Cauca River from Traditional Knowledge *Carolina Salcedo Portilla, Universidad del Valle*

The Upper River Cauca Basin (URCB) has twenty water quality monitoring stations, which are intended to monitor pollution

trends and provide information on the state of the river through the measurement of physiochemical and microbiological parameters. Through a participatory monitoring system, this research seeks to reconstructing the memory and dialogue with fishing communities as the main actors that have coexisted with the river for decades. The value of changes in fishing activity of the URBC will be carried out in two specific areas; the first of these, La Bolsa, where there are high water quality indices, and the second, Mediacanoa, which presents low-quality indices. It shows how fishing species are affected and how these changes, despite the quality of the water or specific phenomena, have transformed their history and relationship with the river. In this sense, it is expected that the assessment of URBC ecosystem integrity from different perspectives, considering the river as an integral ecosystem and knowing the ecosystem services it provides to the communities established in its surroundings.

To Phone for Fish: Global Flows and Embodied Skills Among Specialized Sierra Leone Divers *Cecilie Baann, Aarhus University*

Drawing on ethnographic research in a Sierra Leone fishing town, I explore how shifting global flows of extraction entangle with livelihood practices and skills among fishermen. Whereas the majority of the fishermen attune their bodies and set of skills to the water surface, be it by spotting dark-coloured areas or unusual ripples that moves against the current, the last decade has seen the growth of a new profession within the fishing industry. Known as phonemen, translating to “the men who phone/call to fish”, they operate instead under water. Their body is specialized to listen through water, and locating the “talking” bobo croaker fish. I analyze the growth of the specialized phonemen divers through a history of shifting extractions from the Gulf of Guinea and West Africa at large. By thinking with water (Chen et.al 2013), both as the experiential substance affecting and affected by bodies, and as evoking our intrinsic multispecies relationality, I argue that the case of the Sierra Leone phonemen can reconfigure colonial histories of extractive relations. Although the new profession could be analysed as local adaptation to a new global flow, this time the Korean demand for the bobo croaker fish, providing only this narrative reduce local practice to realignment with the dominant. Instead, taking the phonemen’s practice of being with water, and attuning their bodies to the ‘tunes of the sea’, seriously in their political and economic consequences, their embodied skills showcase how global flows can be reconfigured to serve local purposes, while enhancing more sustainable methods of marine extraction, through the use of selective fishing methods.

Stranger Tides: Investigating the Restoration of Good Relations with Transcontinentally-Entangled Ecologies *Salina Suri, Harvard University - History of Science*

For centuries, the shipping industry has been responsible for the transoceanic exchange of species, both human and other-than-human, made possible through ballast. Since 1852, ships have used water as a stabilizing mechanism, intaking water at their port of origin to prevent capsizing on the high seas (Davidson and Simkanin 2012). Unbeknownst to the engineers that designed this system, the aquatic species that had previously made their communities in what became ballast water would also be borne across oceans. Ballast water thus teems with complex life, and aquatic stowaways meet foreign ecologies when these waters are released at the port of destination (Helmreich 2009). In this paper, I thicken the histories of ballast communities, questioning when and how scientists became aware that ballast water is not static, but rather introduces new lifeforms to planetary waterways with each voyage. I argue that thinking-with these transcontinentally-entangled ecologies is fundamental to enriching human relations with water as the climate crisis becomes more urgent. To make this argument, I draw on evidence from newspaper articles, legal standards, national and international water regulations, and museum installations. I use a

theoretical framework that incorporates Indigenous STS and Animal Studies to analyze these works, with a particular focus on pluriversal and otherwise possibilities in water governance. Using the Great Lakes as my site of analysis, I question the ways in which a more dynamic and nuanced understanding of water, its mutability and its role as both habitat and vector, can restore good relations between humans and waterways across coastal borderlands.

Session Organizer:

Dana Burton, George Washington University

Chair:

Shweta Krishnan, George Washington University

317. How can COVID-19 contact tracing promote fair, inclusive, and just health technologies?

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This roundtable addresses the use and effectiveness of COVID-19 contact-tracing efforts and their implications for health technologies through an exchange of views and experiences of local public health leaders, community members, and academic researchers. Taking a sociotechnical, rather than techno-solutionist, standpoint, we approach automated contact tracing as a socially-contextualised and socially-situated practice. Automated contact tracing must be understood as embedded within a broad ecosystem of pandemic responses and contextual factors, including traditional contact-tracing efforts, historical precedents, and local and national governance. Our roundtable focuses on the London Borough of Hackney as a case study to consider contact tracing within these rich contextual frameworks. Hackney is an ethnically and linguistically diverse London borough, with high levels of poverty and inequality, and a significant digital divide. Hackney initially experienced high rates of COVID-19 infection and has undertaken innovative approaches to meet the pandemic’s public health challenges. Together we will explore how digital tracing apps are inextricably linked with a range of other factors, explain what local pandemic-response technologies are being developed on the ground, and consider what Hackney’s experiences with COVID-19 contact tracing can teach us about fair, inclusive, and just health technologies more generally.

Presenters:

Andrew Trathen, London Borough of Hackney

Yewande Okuleye, University of Leicester

Stephanie Hare, Independent scholar and broadcaster

Session Organizer:

Richard McKay, University of Cambridge

318. Innovation and Inequality in Health and Medicine - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

This session investigates how experimental medicine, novel therapeutics, emerging medical technologies, and new diagnostics shape, maintain, and connect to social inequalities. The session addresses how race, gender, class, and other forms of social stratification impact access to and the development of innovative medicine. We are interested in who receives new therapeutics, to which problems or conditions medical attention and innovation attend, and the role of trials and experimentation. Papers might address questions such as: Who stands to benefit from emerging medicine? Who can access new therapies once they are commodified? How are funds and attention applied to - or withheld from - different types of disease? How does medicine drive or reproduce social inequalities? How are vulnerable people or bodies selected as test subjects for emerging therapeutics? We also invite papers that engage with the conference theme and address instances of good (or better) relations among researchers, participants, therapeutics, and illness communities. Here, we seek to consider if and how medical innovations respond to social inequalities, and if we can imagine a more equitable and just approach to experimental medicine. We welcome papers that tie STS research and theory to these concerns and are interested in a broad range of topics and approaches that address tensions between innovation and inequality.

Participants:

Good relations? Practices of Diminishing Inequalities in Pacemaker Implantation in the Global South and Companion Species *Nelly Oudshoorn, University of Twente*

Although reuse of technical devices is an increasingly common practice, creating a second life for high-tech medical implants is more exceptional. The reuse of these devices requires the making of new niches in the highly regulated world of medicine. Based on a case study of pacemaker reuse, this paper addresses two of these niches: pacemaker reutilization in health care in the Global South and implantation practices in dogs in the Global North. I will argue that these reuse practices can be understood as spaces in which cardiologists and veterinary practitioners engage in articulating good relations with respectively low-income heart patients and companion species (Haraway 2003). Because of the global inequality of access to pacemakers, American cardiologists involved in the MyHeartYourHeart project consider the repair of this disparity as their 'moral duty' (Oudshoorn 2020). Veterinary practitioners articulate their practice of implanting recycled pacemakers in dogs as 'a way of honouring all the animals who have been sacrificed in the development of these technologies'. Reused pacemakers are thus articulated as tools that contribute to creating good relations between wealthy and poor nations in terms of equal access to high-tech medicine on the one hand, and humans and companion species on the other hand. Comparing and contrasting these reuse practices, I conclude that making good relations has unintended consequences. Whereas the reuse of pacemakers in poor economies reinforces inequalities in access to new pacemakers, reuse in dogs contributes to inequalities between people who can easily afford the expensive implantation and those who cannot.

Innovating altruism in the context of novel cancer therapeutics *Marlaine Figueroa Gray, KPWHRI*

We are at a unique point in medical history in which emerging cancer therapies can achieve a durable response for previously incurable cancers. From the blunt instrument of traditional chemotherapy to the use of immunotherapies which harnesses a patient's own immune system, patients have volunteered to participate in early phase clinical trials with various levels of risk and benefit. Different types of altruism exist in this liminal space – from participating in a trial to help future others, to consenting to research to advance science, to easing the burden of family members who suffer when there are no clinical options upon which to hang their hope. This study asks: what types of hope are offered and taken up by patients in Phase 1 immunotherapy trials? How do narratives of participation include, or not include, notions of altruism? Can hope for personal benefit and altruism, which has been conceived of in research ethics, in the literature and in practice as a "selfless act" coexist? Who has access to trials, and so has access to hope? Who is excluded and why? What types of relations do various conceptions of altruism and hope create among participants, their families, and their providers? Drawing on fieldwork and interviews with patients who have participated in Phase 1 immunotherapy trials and the providers who care for them, this work will engage with scholars who examine how hope in the contexts of high medical uncertainty helps patients envision a life worth living as a socially situated being (Jensen 2016), how patient hope changes during the course of treatment (Kristiansen 2014), and how conventional conceptions of altruism need to be reimagined to encompass how selflessness is manifested in immunotherapy trials.

Necropolitical Care and Hemodialysis In Rural China *Xisai Song, Cornell University*

Hemodialysis is a life-sustaining treatment for patients suffering from kidney failure. It is notoriously known as a "half-way technology" that jams patients into a chronic and torturing status between life and death. New pharmaceuticals and therapeutics

have been continuously innovated to ameliorate complications and to improve the life quality of patients on hemodialysis. This paper presents an ethnographic study based on my year-long fieldwork in the hemodialysis ward of a county public hospital in China. I focus on examining how poor rural patients struggle with itchy skin, a common but extremely irritating complication of hemodialysis. Particularly, I trace the material and symbolic contours of Sevelamer, an imported drug that helps reduce high blood phosphorus levels and relieve itchy skin. Sevelamer is not only expensive but also available in selective top-tier hospitals. In the ward, I witnessed some patients buy Sevelamer in online patient groups, while others obtained copycat drugs from India through black markets. There were also patients who chose to endure the irritation or turn to cheap options like seeing a sorcerer, calling their herb soup their Sevelamer. In this paper, through examining how poor rural patients try to get or get away from Sevelamer, I show that pharmaceutical innovation is unevenly applied to patients of different socio-political positions. I argue that the biomedical care of hemodialysis is a necropolitical form of care that suffering and death are unequally distributed in a subtle and legitimate way.

The Product is You: Innovation, inequality, and the development of medical treatments. *Michael Halpin, Dalhousie University; Dagoberto Cortez, The University of Texas at Austin*

How are social inequalities tied to the development of novel therapeutics? To answer this question, we analyze multiple qualitative datasets, including interview and ethnographic data collected from various clinics specializing in the research and treatment of cancer, Huntington Disease, and psychosis. By drawing on Goffman's work on the interaction order and STS research that focuses on the pharmaceutical industry, we demonstrate how research participants, clinicians, and researchers are tied to the product development interests of pharmaceutical companies. Our analysis suggests three thematic findings: 1) Inducement: how research participants and clinical researchers are encouraged and/or incentivized to engage in research on novel therapeutics; 2) Gate Keeping: how research participants and clinical researchers must participate in research on novel therapeutics to access resources; 3) The pharmaceutical order: how pharmaceutical companies leverage their resources to pressure research participants', clinicians', and researchers' actions to align with pharmaceutical interests. Inducement, gatekeeping, and the pharmaceutical order maintain dynamic and complicated pathways through which inequality is supported and reconstituted. We discuss our findings in relation to STS work on experimental medicine and sociological research on medicalization. Drawing on the conference theme, we also discuss the potential for different ways of doing therapeutic innovation.

Session Organizer:

Michael Halpin, Dalhousie University

Chair:

Dagoberto Cortez, The University of Texas at Austin

319. Interrogating STS as Critical Pedagogy II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

In Summer 2021, the NSF-funded 'STS as a Critical Pedagogy Workshop' occurred over four separate online sessions, with approximately 35 participants, primarily from the United States. This panel presents papers from participants in the workshop that reflect on practices of teaching and learning STS across a variety of domains, from engineering to art & media, both inside higher ed and beyond. These papers offer novel ways of conceptualizing and implementing critical STS pedagogies even as they interrogate what STS as critical pedagogy might mean.

Participants:

Windows of Opportunity: Role Playing STS Theories *Nicole*

Mogul, --Please Select--; David Tomblin, University of Maryland, College Park

Role play is a promising method for delivering content of any kind, including complex STS theory. In STS courses, we often attempt to illustrate STS theory through neatly packaged case studies. This pedagogical approach illustrates the practical application of STS theory, but potentially has the unintended side effect of black-boxing how and why these cases exist. It also allows students to view these cases from a distanced, unempathetic perspective. Furthermore, good case studies are daunting to craft. Role play can help instructors navigate these challenges and can be readily applied to current and historical case studies. We present role play as a co-constructive approach to creating case studies with students and understanding STS theory. This contributes to STS as critical pedagogy by providing a framework for practitioners to engage undergraduates with complex STS theory. Inspired by open-framing, narrative discovery approaches to public engagement (Macnaghten 2017), we asked students to adopt stakeholder roles from the 2021 Texas winter storm energy/water infrastructure disaster in an Infrastructure and Society course. We describe how we deployed this activity to simultaneously help students co-construct a case study through the discovery of stakeholder narratives and unpack sociotechnical transitions theory (Geels et al. 2017). We explore how combining role play with learning STS theory can help students critically engage with case study development. This empowers students to define the parameters of a case study and gain empathy for stakeholders. We show that this approach literally and concretely helps students situate themselves and other stakeholders within STS theory.

Grappling with gender and sexual orientation in introductory biology courses *Shelby Dietz, Cornell University*

In the past two decades the goals of inclusive science education have moved beyond demographic inclusion toward fully embracing “the challenge to the values and standards of science and science education” (Barton, 1998) by critiquing “schools and education as institutions and processes that limit possible identities, promote binary constructions, and naturalize heteronormativity” (Gunckel, 2009). At the introductory undergraduate college level the centrality of reproductive coupling profoundly informs instruction in biology, particularly in discussion of evolutionary theory and sex-specific characteristics and behaviors. However, increasingly diverse and activist undergraduate populations demand that the biology curriculum confronts unexamined assumptions about the “purpose” of sexuality and sex roles. In this paper I will describe how three undergraduate biology courses have responded to student questions about gender and sexuality as presented in course materials, and how we have explored pedagogical tools with which to engage this student interest. I will also address how online instruction during the pandemic has affected how students interact with peers and with traditional authoritative voices as they discuss gender and sexuality in this changed (and charged) landscape of knowledge production. Works cited: Barton, A. (1998). *Feminist science education*. New York: Teachers College Press. Gunckel, K. L. "Queering science for all: Probing queer theory in science education." *Journal of Curriculum Theorizing* 25.2 (2009): 48-61.

Working Genre Form as an Experimental STS Lab Practice *Briana Leone, Drexel University; Alison Kenner, Drexel University; Morgan Sarao, Drexel University Center for Science, Technology, and Society (STS); Atharva Bhagwat, Drexel University; Sean Huberth, Drexel University; Cameron LaPorte, Drexel University; Andrew Rosenthal, Drexel University; The Energy Rights Project, Drexel University; The PECE Design Team, University of California, Irvine*

Puzzling is a long-used pedagogical framework that prompts

students to work through materials, often in collaboration with others, and in ways that can resist hierarchy and linearity. In hands-on activities, where students disassemble and/or reassemble theory and data materially, puzzling as pedagogical form plays with temporality and ordering logics; rethinks access to content at different scales; and can invert relationships between data and theory. In this presentation we look at how the Platform for Experimental and Collaborative Ethnography (PECE) enables “puzzle” work -- as one student put it -- in the construction of research projects. Material for this presentation is drawn from two distinct STS labs held at Drexel University (in 2017 and 2020), as well as from the experiences of undergraduate researchers. In labs, students work throughout the term to gather “artifacts” (i.e. data visualizations, scholarly publications, reports, videos, interview transcripts, and participant observations) that can be curated in a “PECE essay”, an emergent form of scholarly publishing that students came to think of as puzzle design. In one lab, the essay had to be collaboratively authored, which forced questions about publication design, equity in authorship, and multiplicity in narrative voice. In this paper, we draw on Trinh T. Minh-ha’s work to suggest that PECE essays -- as both practice and product -- demand that “one listens to the intervals of ‘evidences’” (2013), the space between distinct pieces of data, and to think of research projects as assemblages with resonance.

The Pedagogical Commonlands *Emily York, James Madison University; Shannon N. Conley, James Madison University*

Critical participation provides a framework for theorizing STS practices of engagement and intervention that reflexively stay open to mutual flows of learning even as they work to radically challenge dominant assumptions about the social and technical (Downey and Zuiderent-Jerak, 2017). As taken up in STS pedagogies, critical participation sits well with critical pedagogies that attend to teaching as co-learning with students and that challenge structures of power in and outside the classroom. It also reframes the classroom as a site of engagement and intervention where STS knowledges might be co-produced, not just disseminated. Moreover, viewing STS pedagogies through a lens of critical participation makes visible the possibility that STS pedagogies themselves might constitute a practice of critical participation not only with students but with experts and administrators across disciplines within an institution. This paper begins to theorize the ‘pedagogical commonlands’ as both phenomenon and strategy, drawing on analysis of a series of engagements in the STS Futures Lab at James Madison University. In these engagements, the pedagogical frame of the space and the event--in this case, the STS Futures Lab and the ‘Co-Imagining Futures’ workshops--orientates invited experts to approach the interaction as an opportunity for teaching and learning. This facilitates an openness to cross-disciplinary dialogue in which STS knowledges can be taken up in ways that might be more challenging outside of this pedagogical focus. The pedagogical commonlands--building on Marilyn Strathern’s *Commons and Borderlands*--focuses attention on the ways that STS as critical pedagogy might leverage shared interest and pleasure in teaching and learning (formally and informally) to facilitate critical participation in a variety of spaces.

Session Organizer:

Emily York, James Madison University

Discussant:

Marisa R Brandt, Michigan State University

320. What we talk about when we talk about depth – II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Recent scholarship on mining and drilling, urban infrastructure, maritime logistics, the transit of toxins, the anthropocene, and the disposal of bodies theorizes the politics of sub-surface worlds (Anand 2017, Appel et al. 2015,

Campling & Colás 2021, Klinger 2017, Murphy 2013, Yusoff 2018). Bringing these depths into view has centered new spaces, scales, materials, and relations. Yet the concept of depth itself, and the responsibilities that attend its investigation, have not been sufficiently examined. Depth is more than a simple spatial signifier or linguistic trope. Thinking with and beyond verticality (Graham and Hewitt 2012), volumetric space (Weizman 2007, Elden 2013, Billé 2018), and metaphor (McKittrick 2018, Shalem 2017), we want to suggest that the deeps constitute a semiotic landscape that is resolutely material but always exceeds conventional materialist readings. Deep spaces matter: they are simultaneously material and meaningful. This panel engages critically and creatively with the mattering of chthonic landscapes, defined broadly. Encoded in the concept of depth are all kinds of latent associations and meanings. As such, we may speak of deep time, deep sleep, deep ecology, deep learning, the deep state, skin deep, diving deep, depth of character, depth of perception, depth of field, depth of meaning, etc. How, we ask, are these (and many other) conceptualizations of depth tied to the deep places of the earth? And if, as Spivak teaches us, thought must be “written on the planet as planet” (2012: 349), how does thinking operate beneath the planetary surface?

Participants:

“A resource in and of itself”: Grid-scale batteries, deep decarbonization, and the politics of energy storage *Caroline Celeste White-Nockleby, Massachusetts Institute for Technology (MIT)*

Grid-scale batteries – which attach to the electricity grid to buffer supply and demand – figure as increasingly central protagonists in calls for deep decarbonization. Batteries promise a more palatable profundity than fossil fuel reserves – offering increasingly “deep cycles” that can hold, and release, energy for long durations to discipline the unruly schedules of sun and wind supplies. This temporal and chemical depth also confers, like coal and oil, accumulative potential: as a means to store electricity, a uniquely ephemeral commodity, batteries mediate power. For those with access, batteries thus promise to sustain the grid as unmarked ground: they can regularize electricity provision at multiple scales, insulating against infrastructural decline, climate-inflected blackouts, and energy insecurity. Yet batteries are inescapably extractive. As a “fuel-neutral” resource, they make electrons sourced from sun and gas alike “more efficient, productive, and competitive” [2]. Projections of battery growth, moreover, increasingly authorize and compel projects to mine and stockpile “critical minerals”. Here, I draw on an “interface ethnography” of corporate battery marketing materials to trace the continuities between extraction, aspirations for grid reliability, and decarbonization. In what ways, I ask, do the evolving dimensionalities of energy storage reconfigure, or sustain, power? How is depth, as both metaphor and dimension, deployed – and effaced – in decarbonization futurities? [1] Orner, Sherry B. “Access: Reflections on Studying up in Hollywood.” *Ethnography* 11, no. 2 (June 1, 2010): 211–33. [2] Energy Storage Association. “Energy Storage Pairs Well with All Grid Assets.” 2018. <https://energystorage.org/wp/wp-content/uploads/2019/09/2018.10.12-1-pager-on-paired-storage.pdf>.

The burdens of benchmarking on abundance: towards a relational ontology of electricity systems *Veronica I Jacome, Temple University*

Critical electricity infrastructure literature leans on an old global dichotomy: infrastructure in the global north is taken-for-granted and largely invisible, while in the global south, access is highly unreliable, problematic, and a source of every-day scrutiny and precarity. This tension between the visible and invisible underscores the very nature of energy development today. Electricity’s long history of capitalist development, nation-building, and colonial interrelations have produced what I call “abundant” systems, those characterized by cheap, constant, plenty, invisible access, and “constrained” systems, those characterized by costly, intermittent, uncertain, visible access.

Moreover, while electricity infrastructure in sub-Saharan Africa is largely understood through its failures, it is a so-called successful, abundant infrastructure that needs reevaluation. In this work I leverage this energy dichotomy in an attempt to move beyond it and develop a relational ontology of postcolonial energy infrastructure. I explore African cities’ unreliable electricity systems not only through what renders it visible—its erratic and dynamic nature—but through its relationship to invisible infrastructure. Here, I see theoretical and practical merit in scrutinizing abundant systems, which benchmark constrained systems, but often ignored. Ultimately, I argue it is the bias of abundance in infrastructure that shapes our understanding of, and relationship to, constrained systems.

The deep time of Bitcoin: Excavating the “work” in proof-of-work cryptocurrency mining *Zane Griffin Talley Cooper, University of Pennsylvania, Annenberg School for Communication*

Estimates place Bitcoin’s current energy consumption at 78.04 terawatt-hours/year, an amount comparable to the nation of Chile (Digiconomist, 2021). While Bitcoin’s energy problem has become increasingly visible in both academic and popular discourse (see Lally et al. 2019; Stoll et al. 2019), the computational mechanisms through which the Bitcoin network “mines” coins, proof-of-work, has gone under-examined. This paper interrogates the “work” in proof-of-work mining. What is this work? How can we access its material history? I trace this history through a media archaeology of the bit, in an attempt to better situate the intimate relationship between information and energy in proof-of-work systems. I argue the “work” in these systems is principally heat-work, and trace its ideological constructions back to nineteenth-century thermodynamic science, and the reframing of doing work as something exhaustible, directional, and irreversible (Prigogine & Stengers 2017; Daggett 2019). I then follow thermodynamic discourse through Cybernetics debates in the 1940s, illustrating how, early in the formation of Information Theory, the heat-work undergirding the functioning of a “bit” was obscured and compartmentalized, allowing information to be productively abstracted apart from its energetic infrastructures (Beniger 1986; Hayles 1999; Kline 2015). I conclude with a discussion of the heat-work within the Application Specific Integrated Circuit (ASIC), Bitcoin’s principal mining tool, arguing that proof-of-work mining is not a radical exception to the computing status quo, but rather a lens through which to think more broadly about computing’s complex relationship to energy, and ultimately, how this relationship can be different.

The underground as a transition space : the case of a hazardous waste storage in France *Lisa Claussmann, CERME3 INSERM U988*

The ever-renewed promise of improving our daily life through technology has invested the environment right down to underground space. However, the risks linked to the increasing complexity of science and technology are not controllable, defining our society as a “risk society” (Beck, 1986). To speak of “depth” is therefore to take into account the unpredictability of the world and the scientific uncertainties about terrestrial movements. In the case of underground space for hazardous waste storage, these depths are multiple and mix the mining imagination of the past with the promises of a better future. Thus, storing hazardous waste in the subsurface was presented in the 1990s as a means of protecting the environment. This paper will show how different kinds of depths can be mobilized as industrial and ecological transition spaces. It is based on a case study of an underground site of ultimate hazardous waste in Wittelsheim, France. The site is located around 530 meters below a groundwater table and 25 meters under the layer of formerly mined potash. Between 1999 and 2002, a total of 44 011 tons of hazardous waste were stored underground. This paper will start

by focusing on social mobilizations of depths as receptacles for past and future stories. Then, it will study how the groundwater table, the former mine and the disposal site are considered, jointly or in opposition to each other, by political and industrial actors. This work is based on an investigation combining archives, interviews and observations of the underground waste disposal.

Session Organizers:

Anya Kaplan-Seem, University of Minnesota
Xander Lenc, University of California, Berkeley
Nicholas Anderman, University of California, Berkeley

Chair:

Xander Lenc, University of California, Berkeley

Discussant:

Julie Michelle Klinger, University of Delaware

321. STS as Whiteness? Towards Decentering Whiteness in STS - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

In 2018, Michael Mascarenhas described STS as a white space through how its programs, institutions, leadership, and inquiries perpetuate white supremacy. This often emerges as colorblindness, an ideology of unmarked whiteness where anti-racism is assumed to accomplish anti-racism. Although existing STSers work to decenter United States and European geographies and genealogies as the sole sites for STS, many sites of whiteness in STS remain black boxed. Given the position of STS to shape and intervene in technoscientific knowledge production and policy, it is urgent for STSers to actively deconstruct the whiteness that is reproduced in our work. In thinking with the conference theme of Good Relations and the urgency of making and doing STS in ways that decenter white supremacy, presenters will explore what it means for STS and STSers to decenter white supremacy. This includes discussions about the reproduction of whiteness in STS and the alternative relationalities required to decenter whiteness in our scholarship and practice. Over the course of two sessions, presentations will address questions, including, but not limited to: How does STS (including tacit notions of who/what is STS) reproduce whiteness? How might pressures to institutionalize STS or form disciplinary identities foreground whiteness? How could discussions about the whiteness of STS mask existing critical race, postcolonial, decolonial, and ethnic studies scholarship in STS? What possibilities are there for decentering whiteness in conceptual frameworks, pedagogies, scholarship, programs, and practices of STS? How might we strategize such that non-white scholars are not disproportionately burdened to decenter whiteness?

Participants:

Approaches to Decolonization in Data and Algorithms *Megan M Rim*, University of Michigan

This paper considers the decolonial turn in examinations of data and algorithms and takes as its foundation and roadmap the essay by Eve Tuck and Wayne Yang, "Decolonization is not a metaphor." It examines a few approaches that analyze these relations through the lens of colonizing powers. Looking at the centrality of North America and other settler colonial contexts to much of this scholarship, it asks what a consideration of settler colonialism does to these frameworks. Through a discussion of some of Tuck and Yang's central claims, this paper begins to critically explore the potential resonances and pitfalls of this decolonial turn with some self-reflexive consideration of the author's BIPOC settler positionality. Centering its discussion on the current theme of 'good relations', this paper considers, in particular, the possibilities of decolonial studies of data and algorithms that resist what Tuck and Yang, inspired by Janet Mawhinney, refer to as, "settler moves to innocence," which they describe as "those strategies or positioning that attempt to relieve the settler feelings of guilt or responsibility without giving up land or power or privilege, without having to change much at all" (2014: 10). That is, it asks what a real engagement with the project of decolonization that centers Indigenous concerns looks

like in the study of data and algorithms. Tuck, E., & Yang, K. W. (2012). Decolonization is not a metaphor. *Decolonization: Indigeneity, education & society*, 1(1).

From Stages to Styles: How Feminist Technoscience has Shaped and is Shaped by Constructionist Learning Theory
Michael Lachney, Michigan State University; *Stephanie Jennings*, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Constructionist learning theory is a dominant paradigm underpinning educational technology. A defining feature is its epistemological shift from linear developmental stages to pluralistic learning styles. This is largely what distinguishes Jean Piaget's constructivism from Seymour Papert's constructionism. Little attention has been paid to what motivated this shift, namely feminist technoscience. Like Piaget, Papert drew on socially and culturally situated understandings of science to theorize and study children's epistemologies. But unlike Piaget, Papert did believe in a single scientific method but instead a multiplicity of styles that could include formal thinking, but also concrete styles based on proximity and anthropomorphization. But how did Papert come to this pluralistic image of scientific knowledge production? I show how Papert developed constructionism by leveraging theory and research from feminists who were studying science, scientists, and knowledge production. From feminists (e.g. Haraway 1979; Merchant, 1980; Harding and Hintikka 1983), Turkle and Papert (1992) showed how the gender politics of science have traditionally constructed objective distance and the scientific method as masculine. They then turned to feminist who showed how scientists use a plurality of styles to successfully produce knowledge, breaking down the hierarchy of the abstract over the concrete in the process (Keller 1985). Today, feminist images of knowledge production continue to shape constructionist research and practice (Resnick 1997) and feminist technoscientists now draw on constructionism to shape their own work, including anti-racist computing education and collaborating during environmental disasters (Eglash 2017; Fortun 2016).

Decentering Whiteness in Teaching History of Technology: Notes Toward a How-To *Janet Abbate*, Virginia Tech

Popular books such as Ibram X. Kendi's *How to Be an Antiracist* and Crystal Fleming's *How to Be Less Stupid About Race* frame antiracism within the how-to genre, emphasizing the need to actively question and dismantle practices that privilege whiteness. Translating this broad political mandate into the specifics of STS pedagogy, however, raises both practical and philosophical challenges. This paper focuses on my efforts to decenter whiteness within a small domain of STS practice: a history of technology course. Nina Lerman's influential 2010 essay, "Categories of Difference, Categories of Power: Bringing Gender and Race to the History of Technology," argues that race and gender bias construct boundaries around whose activities count as "technology," resulting in the "naturalized exclusion" of women and people of color from historical scholarship. The first iteration of my course reflected this bias in its topics and readings. In order to include more diverse authorship and broader experiences of technology, I had to question the very definition of technology and what topics belonged to its history. My revised syllabus focuses less on invention and more on use and maintenance; less on industrialization and more on agriculture; less on the West and more on peripheries. I will describe strategies and obstacles encountered in this imperfect and ongoing effort to decenter whiteness in STS teaching.

4S Got Bodied by MC Hammer and Deserved It: Race, Social Media, and the State of STS *Joshua Earle*, Virginia Tech

On February 22nd MC Hammer (yes that one, no I'm not kidding), tweeted what is perhaps the most succinct thesis statement of STS I've ever seen: "when you measure include the measurer." In the hours that followed, STS twitter understandably went absolutely wild. Then 4S tweeted in

response something so condescending that every Black person felt it in their bones. They asked what we might suggest as additional reading for Hammer “now that he’s a budding STS scholar.” The fallout from that one, poorly-worded tweet I believe has significantly harmed the STS community among people of color, especially black aspirants. I also believe that it is the result of a culture of exclusion and whiteness that STS as a field has failed to solve in its nearly 40 year history. At the 40th anniversary 4S meeting Michael Mascarenhas gave a keynote about the lack of racial diversity in the field, and in its topics of discussion at our meetings. It was described as “thrilling” and received a thunderous standing ovation. This was in 2015. This year, the Open Panels show very little improvement on the trends Macharenhas described. I argue that we need to take a long hard look at ourselves and begin to fix the culture that we have built where not a single Open Panel on Transgender issues, only one on Disability Issues, and only two that specifically reference Blackness (out of 5 total that mentioned race) were submitted. Out of 210.

Session Organizer:

Gabriel Medina-Kim, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Discussant:

Michael Mascarenhas, 856 Jones St

322. The Boundaries of Universality – Contemporary Engagements of Science II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

In recent years, the idea that science represents universal facts has been challenged from a variety of perspectives. While scientific approaches remain a compelling and normative force in people’s ways of thinking, acting and feeling in the world, disparate alliances from across the political spectrum – anti-vaxxers, climate-change sceptics, Covid-19 deniers, but also movements informed by postcolonial critique – fundamentally call into question the status of science and its claims to universality. Today, it is necessary to ask not only “whose science”, where, and for whom, but also to investigate how people engage, or resist science’s universality. In this panel, we investigate contemporary political mobilizations with, for, and against science in fields as varied as astronomy, biomedicine, psychology, genetics, field biology, and artificial intelligence. Specifically, we are interested in the boundaries of science and the limits to its universal applicability. When, and around which issues, does universality become mobilized and contested? What are the politics behind specific attempts to universalize and/or localize knowledge? Where do claims to universality enact inclusive and/or exclusive socialities? The papers in this panel deal with the “boundary work” of science as it moves through, and is modified in, different contexts. Our common assumption is that science’s universality is not absolute, but contingent and relational. What counts as science, or as universal, is always enacted and negotiated in practice. Anthropological exploration of the mutability and mobility of universalizing and localizing dynamics in the sciences offers valuable perspectives for reflections on our own scientific practices.

Participants:

Alternative Science: Knowledge Production among Covid-19 Deniers **Hynek Bečka**, *Institute of Anthropology - University of Leipzig*

The discourses questioning the legitimacy of the Western biomedicine are gaining new urgency during the covid-19 pandemic. While the people who promote such narratives are usually described as “anti-science,” they rarely reject science entirely. Rather, according to their own narratives, anti-vaxxers, anti-maskers, and covid-19 deniers conduct experiments, interpret data, and offer radically different interpretation of medical facts. They often evoke the authority and prestige of chosen medical experts who formulate unorthodox theories using scientific language and terminology. This alternative knowledge is shared and discussed on Facebook groups, YouTube videos, and other social media. This paper is based on mostly digital

ethnographic research among alternative healers, anti-vaxxers, and covid-19 deniers in the Czech Republic. Rather than once again stressing the danger of undermining medical authority during the global pandemic, or tracking the ultimate origin of this “disinformation,” it instead asks how knowledge is created and contested in both digital and physical spaces. In these contexts, scientific universality is both disputed and mobilized, and personal experiences become integrated into a growing global system of alternative knowledge which also has universal ambitions. Exploring moments in which the legitimacy of biomedicine (and science in general) is contested raises questions such as: Whose expertise counts as science? And what forms of knowledge-making are considered legitimate? These questions are especially relevant in the context of global pandemic.

Extending the Boundaries and Participating in the Center – Astronomers in Madagascar **Hanna Nieber**, *Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology*

In Madagascar, astronomy is a relatively new science. While local public discourse often uses the terms “astronomie” and “astrologie” interchangeably, astronomy students are invested in performing boundary work for their discipline. In social media and on the ground, they are active in explaining how to distinguish the universally scientific “astronomie” from the culturally particular “astrologie.” In contrast to calls for decolonization, which often seek ways of doing science differently and take seriously those knowledges that the colonial encounter suppressed, Malagasy astronomy students are not interested in localizing “astronomie.” Rather, they are proudly invested in contributing to global astronomical research and struggle for recognition within astronomical circles. The International Astronomical Union supports this goal, as do initiatives such as “Astronomy in Colour” (and especially “Astronomy in Colour – South Africa”), or “Black Physicists.” Thus, the inclusion of people from across the globe in the project of understanding our planet in the cosmos merges the logics of doing “universal science” and enacting decolonization in particular places. The boundaries of universality appear to unfold with participation in the center of that which is taken to be universal. In my contribution, building largely on social media research, I ask how the participation of Malagasy astronomers in the project of doing “universal science” feeds into calls for decolonization and thereby provides a perspective to query boundaries of science’s universality.

The New Indian Male: Globalized Bodily Ideals vs. Local Layering and Technologies of Self-Fashioning **Michiel Baas**, *Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology*

Recent economic growth in India has come with new and highly specific ideas of the ideal male body which deviate considerably from earlier bodily and associated masculine ideals. While an older generation of middle-class men took pride in their “health potbelly,” signifying prosperity and wellbeing, a younger generation now gravitates toward a lean, muscular ideal. As a result, fitness centers have become an indelible part of the Indian urban landscape, and bodybuilding and male modeling competitions have witnessed a surge in popularity. Physically this body resonates with a globalized ideal of lean muscularity and vascularity. Concomitant notions of health, longevity and quality of life also color the debate about such bodies in Indian media. However, this paper will counter this “universalized” image by asking with what other meanings this body is imbued with within a local Indian-urban context. Drawing on extensive fieldwork among fitness trainers who often also compete in bodybuilding and modeling competitions, the paper discusses how the process of bodily transformation offers insight into what the (imagined) muscular body communicates inside the gym, on-stage at competitions, and “outside,” to a broader audience in day-to-day life.

Session Organizers:

Hanna Nieber, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology
Julia Vorhöfner, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology
Claudia Lang, Institute of Anthropology - University of Leipzig

Samiksha Bhan, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology

Chair:

Desirée Kumpf, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology

Discussant:

Hanna Werner, Max-Weber-Kolleg, University of Erfurt

323. Genealogies of the Human in AI Systems II.

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

From rational actors to addicted users, Eurocentric theories of mind and society inform the design of AI/ML systems, both explicitly and through uninterrogated universalising norms and assumptions. Scholarly work has examined the societal impacts of AI systems, but less has been done to examine the assumptions of the social that inform such systems. This panel explores a genealogy of the human in the machine, examining AI systems as a palimpsest of conceptions of mind and society inherited from the fields that feed into AI research including cognitive science, behavioural psychology, economics, and philosophy. We seek to tease apart the models and paradigms of the human that are translated into code, used to act on, navigate, categorise and govern the world. Hubert Dreyfus famously drew on phenomenology to challenge the rationalist assumptions of human intelligence underlying AI research. "Facts and rules"-based theories of intelligence have given way to a neural network paradigm, responding in part to Dreyfus' challenge. Yet the question of what notions of the human are entangled in AI systems remains—calling us to examine not only conceptions of human intelligence—but also human bodies and human social structures. We invite papers examining how paradigms of mind and society are explicitly encoded, invisibly inscribed, and entirely omitted from AI/ML design and exploring the consequences of these encodings and erasures. We are particularly interested in work exploring AI systems as situated in racial capitalism and colonialism and the racialised and gendered dimension of the human as encoded in AI systems.

Participants:

The Artificial View From Nowhere: Interrogating the Ethical and Political Assumptions Underlying Computational Vision
Emily Denton, Google; *Alex Hanna*, Google; *Razvan Amironesei*, Google; *hilary nicole*, Google

In this work, we interrogate the key assumptions of the theory of sight that underlie modern computer vision technologies, finding a problematization of "sight" rooted in a decontextualized and a non-situated, physicalist account of human vision. We examine the disciplines that the field has historically (and currently) engaged with and the accounts of human vision that are used to motivate research agendas and methods. We find that the field engages regularly, and aspirationally with cognitive neuroscience and early childhood learning in a manner that reinforces a universalist and objectivist account of sight. For example, narratives that focus on innate faculties and neural structures serve to frame human perception as disembodied and decontextualized information processing, rather than a situated and contextual process of making sense of and describing the visual world. We also observe theories of early childhood learning being selectively and haphazardly integrated into computer vision discourse and used to motivate new methods. Regular reliance on a child as the canonical viewer further substantiates sight as an amoral non-interpretive act — a child does not judge, interpret, or deliberate upon the scene but simply sees the world as self-evident. In contrast, we observe the field remains largely disconnected from fields of study oriented around semiotics, hermeneutics, phenomenology, and other studies of meaning in relation to the visual world. We close by examining the social implications for the individuals, communities, and cultures that are erased and marginalized by

computer vision technologies built on the illusion of a universal and perpectiveless way of ordering the visual world.

AI, Sinophobia and Sinophilia: Artificial Intelligence and/as the 'Yellow Peril' *Kerry Mackereth*, University of Cambridge

This paper considers how AI is racialised and how AI racialises. It enriches existing reflections on racialisation and AI by examining how Sinophobia and Sinophilia shape the concept of and the field of artificial intelligence, illuminating how the figurations of the 'Orient' and the 'Yellow Peril' permeate contemporary AI discourse. The first section of this paper, 'AI and the Yellow Peril', outlines the tense geopolitical relations between China and the West and how this operates in the field of AI. The second section, 'AI as the Yellow Peril', complicates the framing of AI as white in Katz (2020) and Cave and Dihal (2020) by arguing that certain forms of AI, in particular artificial general intelligence, are racialised as threats to Western civilisation through Yellow Peril discourses. The final section, 'The Yellow Peril as AI', turns to the question of Chinese humanness, its relationship to technology, and how it is both confirmed and denied through processes of racialisation. Building on work by Atanasoski and Vora (2019) and Anne Cheng (2017, 2018), it explores how Chinese (sub-)humanity is produced with, through, and alongside technology, focusing on the racialised representation of Chinese people as distinctly 'machinic'. Drawing on Anne Cheng's provocation that the 'yellow woman' is 'an (if not the) original cyborg' (Cheng 2017), it suggests that perhaps she is also an (if not the) original artificial intelligence. It concludes with some thoughts regarding how critiques of China and Chinese exceptionalism can be made without reproducing the discourse of the Yellow Peril.

Playful Disasters: Mimetic Language, Gender and the Fantasy of Agential Machines *Jamie Steele*, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

This paper reviews patents of natural language processing technologies to explore the ways in which natural language processing (NLP) went from a fundamentally playful mimetic project (Weizenbaum, 1966) to an almost immediate shift towards serious development, with developers intentionally utilizing the "Pygmalion effect" (Switzky, 2020) to lure NLP technology users into a false sense of interacting with thinking, agential machines. Drawing on NLP technology patents, I examine the ways that patent holders conceptualize the Pygmalion effect process as part of their technology and its justification for development, the role that gender plays in facilitating this illusion, and finally the ways in which multiple systems of human interaction – from corporate and academic interests, patent holders, developers and programmers, to end users – color and code these programs as "agential." Through an analysis of the data presented, I situate NLP AI as a coproduction of social, artifactual, and psychological norms which conflates mimetic 'machine minds' with human minds through intentional technological and legal manipulation. Weizenbaum, Joseph. "ELIZA—a computer program for the study of natural language communication between man and machine." *Communications of the ACM* 9, no. 1 (1966): 36-45. Switzky, Lawrence. "ELIZA Effects: Pygmalion and the Early Development of Artificial Intelligence." *Shaw* 40, no. 1 (2020): 50-68.

Algorithms of Distress: Health care workers, automation and moral injury *Alexa Hagerty*, University of Cambridge; *Livia Garofalo*, Northwestern University

Artificial Intelligence has fully entered the realm of medical care, from patient scheduling to patient risk assessment (Obermeyer et al. 2019; Munavalli et al. 2021). In this paper we examine the intersection of AI/ML systems in healthcare and healthcare workers' experiences of "moral injury" and "moral distress." Healthcare providers, especially those trained to deliver care in high-intensity environments like Emergency Rooms and Intensive Care Units, are used to making difficult clinical and

ethical decisions regarding patient care. The medical literature refers to some of these conundrums as producing “moral distress”, i.e. “when one knows the right thing to do, but institutional constraints make it nearly impossible to pursue the right course of action” (Jameton 1984). The COVID-19 pandemic has intensified such distress (Greenberg et al. 2020). We explore the convergence of AI/ML systems and moral distress through examining systems deployed during the pandemic to automate resource allocation, assess and treat healthcare worker “burn out”, as well as a more general promise that automation will free healthcare workers’ time and energy to focus on the most meaningful aspects of their work: patient care. Drawing on the well-known term “idioms of distress”(Nichter 1981, 2010)--meaning the variety of culturally salient ways people express or enact distress--we explore “algorithms of distress” -- the variety of moral affordances, subjectivities, and decision-making practices at the intersection of healthcare workers’ experiences and AI/ML.

Tell me how I Feel: Voice and the Encoding of Corporate Emotions *Sarah Bell, Michigan Technological University*

This paper shows how the emerging discipline of affective computing, based in a computational model of mind, defines human feeling as a machine-readable taxonomy of emotions encoded biometrically, as in the acoustic waveforms of human vocalization. Recent research has challenged the existence of a universal set of human emotions as well as any biometric consistency in emotional expression, finding instead that affect is intensely cultural and its individual expression highly idiosyncratic (Barrett, 2017). Nevertheless, there are a burgeoning number of surveillance systems that feed voice and other data through computational algorithms that purport to decode what a person is feeling. This claim is dependent on a cybernetic model of the human that subordinates the body to being the interface between a symbol-processing brain and its environment. This powerful linking of communication and calculation in the definition of cognition fosters an ideology of “computationalism”—a belief that most human and social experiences can be explained and managed through computer processing. That is, while theories of mind remain actively debated, the brute forces of engineering have fully embraced the computational theory and used it to develop and justify data models that measure and conscript more of the human social world into regimes of computational political economy that often constitute “a renewal of colonial oversight” (Golumbia, 2009) in their increased ability to categorize and control aspects of human sociality that were previously hidden from biopolitical exploitation. I show how this computationalism is operationalized in several patents for detecting emotions using voice signal analysis.

Rethinking the Attention Ecology: Between Technology and Biology *Meredith Root-Bernstein, CNRS UMR CESCO, Muséum*

Current social theories of attention centre on the “attention economy.” In this way of thinking, attention is theorized as a limited resource, and largely conceptualized in binary terms, much like an on/off switch: you are paying attention or you are not. The “attention economy” stems from the historical moment of 19thC industrialization, coinciding with a growing conceptualization of psychological and behavioural self-control, despite suffering, as a form of moral improvement (e.g. Kuklick 2011; Baumeister & Tierney 2011). These moral and economic models underwrite both technology design and critiques of that design. Instead, this paper proposes a theory of “attention ecology” drawn from anthropology and biological sciences. It considers attention as a complex system involving cognitive processes, behaviours, social practices, and environment. In the multispecies “attention ecology” that exists in nature, in the context of which our own attentional capacities evolved, attention is complex--species attempt to entice, elude, surprise,

and detect one another, to interpret signs of the past and to anticipate the future. The natural world is rhythmic yet unpredictable, and sensorily complex, with many qualities, values and uses of attention. The complexity of attention ecologies in nature should make us skeptical of popular claims that new technologies are overloading human capacities. Claims about “distraction” must be read against a baseline expectation of productivity that valorizes concentrated attention. Thus, contemporary claims of distraction must be understood as historically situated in 19th century moral, technological, and economic structures.

Session Organizer:

Alexa Hagerty, University of Cambridge

Chair:

Livia Garofalo, Northwestern University

324. Same Same but Different: Race and Racializations across National, Disciplinary and Temporal Contexts - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

In human diversity research, race is a moving target. It is rarely clearly defined, and takes on different meanings and labels in different contexts, and often reveals itself as racialized connotations of other terms. From an international perspective, it is apparent that while race is used in political and scientific contexts in the USA or Brazil, for example, in continental Europe, by contrast, today it is commonly considered a taboo. This difference is partly rooted in divergent conceptual meanings in different languages, and various political as well as scientific strategies for dealing with the historical burden of the concept. However, even in countries that are largely imagined as post-racial, race remains as an “absent presence” (M’charek/Schramm/Skinner 2014) within other terms in use such as “ethnicity”, “population”, “migrant background”, “biogeographical ancestry”, “metapopulation” etc. In this panel we welcome contributions inquiring into the national, disciplinary and/or temporal specifics of human difference categorizations – with a focus on, but not limited to, the life sciences. We are particularly interested in the shaping of processes of categorization and in the continuity and discontinuity of concepts of group classification across/in different contexts and specific situations. Possible topics include: * entanglements between race and “ethnicity”, “caste”, “populations” etc. * context-specific and language-related differences and similarities between racialized concepts, wordings, meanings, and their historical dis/continuities * travelling concepts, translations, euphemisms, modernizations, and equivocations * processes of racialization in various scientific disciplines * race after race, post-racial racializations, racializations in antiracism * effects of notions like “colourblindness”, “race-consciousness”, “race realism”, “social constructivism” * different bureaucratic-administrative regulations of race, e.g. in the law, in affirmative action, surveys, censuses etc. * attempts to grasp diversity/variation in a non-racialized manner

Participants:

Inclusive genomics, or, don’t mention the (race) war *Emma Kowal, Deakin University*

In national and regional efforts to build genomic reference databases that are inclusive of genomic population diversity, race is an absent presence. In Australia, the primary group requiring inclusion are Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islanders. Large investments in precision medicine are accompanied by various efforts to engage and include Indigenous leaders and research participants. This presentation considers two large laboratories, one in the US and one in Australia, who are building ‘inclusive’ national reference genome databases that will overcome existing ‘translational’ barriers to the implementation of precision medicine. I show that their efforts to generate inclusive databases work (intentionally or unintentionally) to marginalize social science expertise. The work of engaging with Indigenous and other non-white communities falls either to scientists with an ‘interest’ in qualitative methods, or to social scientists who must declare they have no interest in academic publication and are

content to apply their technical expertise to increase minority recruitment. My goal in this presentation is not to chide genome scientists for excluding social scientists or including them only as technical experts. I take a step back from this phenomenon to ask why genome scientists see critical social science as incompatible with 'good' science. I propose that critical social scientists are perceived as a portal to histories and legacies that are viewed as 'not constructive': race, eugenics, justice. I conclude by reflecting on my own attempts to engage 'constructively' with genomic inclusion in Australia by supporting Indigenous scientists: a different approach but not without its own problems.

The (re)configuration of racial surveillance in forensic genetics through forensic DNA phenotyping technology *Filipa Queirós, Centre for Sal Studies, University of Coimbra*

Forensic DNA phenotyping (FDP) technology uses biological samples found at crime scenes to infer probabilistic information about externally visible characteristics of suspects, such as eye, skin and hair colour, and also biogeographic ancestry. Historically linked to controversial debates within the genetics field, race is again under the spotlight since the development of FDP in crime investigations. Embracing a perspective from STS field, this paper discusses the interrelations between forensic genetics and race through the study of expectations towards FDP technology. Underpinned by the concept of contemporary synthesis (Fullwiley, 2014) it explores how FDP combines and conflates ideas about human biological differences that are both race and population-based, and demonstrates how attempts to deconstruct race within science can also, potentially, converge in its reconstruction, (re)creating dynamics of collectivisation of suspicion over specific population groups. Drawing on interviews with forensic geneticists in Germany, the Netherlands, Poland, Portugal and the United Kingdom, the paper explores how their expectations around FDP's development and application (re)invoke race in different domains. Interviewees' narratives reveal both a sensitivity on how FDP may find some resistance in particular EU countries with historical and cultural past experiences' of eugenics and colonialism and a growing perception of its utility as results allow targeting phenotypically othered population groups. By exploring how race is enacted in the context of development and application of FDP technology, the paper also reflects on the slippery nature of race in Europe and how the forensic genetics' shift through intelligence technologies is (re)configuring dynamics of racial surveillance.

Embracing the post-coloniality in molecular anthropology: an ethnography of population genetic labs in Portugal *Ricardo Gomes Moreira, Institute of Social Sciences, University of Lisbon*

When racialized concepts (like "ancestry" or "admixture") are allowed to enter the domain of laboratory work, the stage is set for conflicts between political and scientific interests to emerge (Fullwiley 2007) and to become explicitly integrated into the very core of scientific practice. Knowledge becomes politicized, while power dynamics become more engaged with scientific discursivity (Reardon 2005). In this paper I aim to explore ethnographically two different but complementary types of population genetics practices, as they are articulated by two distinct research groups based in Portugal. Grounded in laboratory ethnographic fieldwork, I intent to describe and reflect about how some more or less underdetermined racial conceptualizations are addressed, dismissed or translated into methodology and knowledge among scientific practitioners, in their organizational, research and negotiation tasks, inside and outside of their scientific institutions. Colonial and post-colonial narratives are strategically articulated and used in the pursuit of what may be considered legitimate scientific practice and aimed to produce scientific and political value, out of the effort to represent external interests in the production of knowledge; as when explicitly inclusive and non-racist scientific policies (Bliss

2012) are combined with the attempts to find access to new collections and research genetic material, or with the calls for medical utility. In sum, I intent to be able to reflect about the ways in which, in this context, some aspects of social identity and recognition become integrated in laboratory materiality and knowledge, while racialized connotations of genetic work are pushed aside from the space of proper science.

Human "Difference" in Precision Medicine Research: Tracing Health Disparities and Race across the Research Lifecourse *Michael Bentz, Columbia University; Emily Vasquez, Columbia University; Nicole Foti, University of California, San Francisco; Stephanie Malia Fullerton, University of Washington; Aliya Saperstein, Stanford University; Janet K. Shim, University of California, San Francisco*

The history of studying human difference and health disparities long predates the advent of precision medicine research (PMR), which aims to tailor treatment and prevention of disease by taking into account individual variability in genes, environment, and lifestyle. Central in this history is the formation of cohort studies, organized in part to investigate the drivers of disparities and modes of intervening upon them. These studies operated with notions of difference, often defined in terms of "race" and lived experience, and ideas about their relations to health disparities that were shaped by the local contexts in which investigators carried out research. In recent years, however, with the widespread pursuit of PMR approaches in cohort studies, categorizations based on genetics and "genetic ancestry" are increasingly invoked in relation to differences that drive health disparities. Drawing on an ethnographic study of PMR cohort studies in the US, this paper traces how PMR shapes what counts as human difference and the downstream effects on causal attributions for and mitigation of health disparities. Our findings illustrate moments of negotiation between and across investigators, disciplines, and geographies about the relevance and meanings of various human differences as cohort studies take up PMR approaches. We expose fundamental tensions between concepts of difference that circulate within and anchor cohort studies across time, and show how these discontinuities shape what is possible in understanding and intervening in health disparities.

Translations of Race in German Epidemiology *Andrea zur Nieden, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany*

This paper explores which categories of human diversity are used in German epidemiology to avoid the term "race", and how they may still carry "absent present" meanings of race (M'charek et al). While in Germany quests for greater inclusion of historically underrepresented groups are increasingly articulated similar to the US, health research is implemented differently in these different national contexts. In the US, political efforts to even out racial/ethnic (and gender) health inequalities have e.g. led to the inclusion of "all relevant groups" in clinical and epidemiological studies, with the underlying notion that these social identities correspond to relatively distinct kinds of biological bodies (Epstein). In Germany, a renaissance of medical and epidemiological (and other life science) research into human diversity is only in the beginning, but an emerging field. Instead of 'race', mostly categories that seem less politically problematic are used, such as "Migrationshintergrund" (migrant background): a formal concept referring to a family history of migration, clearly defined by the German microcensus. On the other hand, "migrant background" is often ethnicised, and essential qualities of race are being ascribed to the group. Different layers of "translation" and racialisation will be described in the talk.

Session Organizers:

Tino Pluemecke, Institute for Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Andrea zur Nieden, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Thiago Pinto Barbosa, Universität Bayreuth

Jenny Reardon, UC Santa Cruz

Veronika Lipphardt, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, University College Freiburg

Chairs:

Nils Ellebrecht, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Mihai Surdu, Research Centre on Antigypsyism/Forschungsstelle Antiziganismus

325. Vectors - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Anything that has both direction and magnitude can be described as a vector. Take a billiard ball. Standing still, it is just a ball. But set in motion, it has new capacities and potentials: it can hit another ball on the table; it can rearrange the board. Or take a mosquito. Alone, it is an insect—ostensibly an isolated being. But once it has been infected with a pathogen, it can spread disease, cause death, change worlds. Toxics, dust storms, super-spreaders: all of these are vectors, too. What can we learn by taking up vectors as objects of analysis? That is, what can we learn by looking at our research objects in their vector forms? We invite contributions from scholars working on a range of objects (medical, environmental, mathematical, political, or otherwise) who are interested in exploring those objects in motion. How do they become relational pathways—entities that spread, link up, cross scales, and expand from points of origin? Can vectors be both problems and blueprints for solving them? Can they be both objects and methods? Does rethinking the object-as-vector invite us to make connections that are otherwise obscure? And what about the researcher-as-vector? Covid-19 throws old ethical quandaries about fieldwork into harrowing relief, pressing questions like: what do “good relations” look like when there is not even a pretense of separation or neutrality? When the scholar-body poses an explicit risk, and is itself at risk, how should that change the ways we go about our work?

Participants:

Vectors of Injustice, or Justice with Lead Feet *Stefanie Graeter*, *The University of Arizona*

In 2006, a local Peruvian rag critiqued municipal responses to endemic lead contamination at the national seaport of Callao as “justice with lead feet.” The phrase evokes two contradicting images: the recalcitrant drag of the dense heavy metal or, when applied to a pedal, a weighty heft productive of illicit accelerations. In Peru, lead generates both of these seemingly disjunctive temporalities of justice, providing a vector for expediting political attention, while, in practice, producing excruciatingly sluggish material transformations. Lead, like its atomic state, is a dense ethical matter. At the turn of the 21st century, newfound scientific research on toxicity jump-started novel political subjectivities, “bodies with minerals,” who mobilized resistance to the ecological harms of Peru’s neoliberal wave of extractive capitalism. Yet, at historical sites of lead contamination, political resolve to remediate these newly inscribed materialities of injustice has remained painfully inert. Accounting for this incongruence, this paper argues that biomedical facts of lead toxicity could not level out the historical rivets of racialized human value, such that as a vector of injustice, the pathway of lead remains obstinately aligned with the same human bodies. As we think collectively in this panel about the direction and magnitude of vectors, this paper asks how STS-oriented ethnographies can productively engage with efforts to break the momentum of (extractive) capitalism and the variegated pathways of its harm.

Uncertainty in Motion: Rumors of a Proxy War *Chloe Ahmann*, *Cornell University*

Between 2012 and 2016, South Baltimore was embroiled in tense

debates about a proposed incinerator, the Fairfield Renewable Energy Project. Those debates were manifestly about local land use, but rumors circulated on both sides that something else was really going on. Opponents of the plant entertained stories, for instance, that that small company behind it was secretly owned by a power-player in the “waste-to-energy” sector, while some supporters swore the campaign to stop it was getting money from Big Landfill. In short: a waste industry proxy war was brewing in South Baltimore. In this paper, I read these rumors as vehicles for interscalar work (Hecht 2018)—as speech acts capable of scaling up, down, and back again to make political claims. On both sides, talk of shadowy outside forces did work to vest some voices with more legitimacy than others. Specifically, each group claimed the mantle of the “local” while suggesting their opponents’ views could only be explained by corporate capture. At the same time, each group admitted doubts about where exactly power lay, coding that opacity as a key part of the problem. In the process of tracking rumors across scales and through allegedly bad relations, I show how talking about the Fairfield Project became a way of commenting on a range of diffuse and ambiguous forces long at work in this part of the city. Ultimately, I propose that rumors are the “vector form” of ambient uncertainty, an abiding structure of feeling in late industrial South Baltimore.

Uncertainty, Mobility, and Nonhuman Border Emergencies in the Margins of Georgia *Gorkem Aydemir*, *George Washington University*

Gali is a so-called frozen conflict zone in the southern borderland of the de facto state of Abkhazia, separated from the rest of Georgia since the end of the Soviet Union. People from Gali have lived under protracted uncertainty and ambivalence for almost three decades. Opposing sovereignty projects—of Georgia, Abkhazia, and Abkhazia’s patron state Russia—impose themselves on people’s movements and rights through isolation, surveillance, and militarization. Despite its unpredictable shifts and arbitrariness, Gali people have generated ways to navigate this borderland over the years to sustain lives that are vitally dependent on formal and informal crossings. Since 2017, however, crises instigated by pests and viruses have introduced an unusual pattern of nonhuman border emergencies that people have to understand and struggle with. By focusing on three successive and related border crises caused by the “invasion” of brown marmorated stinkbugs, H1N1 virus, and COVID-19, this paper explores the new ways that people make sense of the border and the multi-species mobilities that their lives in a seemingly forgotten conflict zone are entangled with.

‘Ungovernable’ Ferns and the Limits of Biodiversity in South India *Pooja Nayak*, *University of Pennsylvania*

How might overabundant ferns vitalize and pressure narratives of place, market, and ecology? Drawing on analyses of multispecies landscapes which challenge the production of territory, this ethnographic paper analyzes the relational worlds of humans and a fern species known as the petridium aquilinum or the ‘bracken fern’ whose slow ‘colonization’ of the Kudremukh National Park in South India threatens the area’s celebrated biodiversity. Ferns were among the earliest flora on earth between 250 to 300 million years ago; recent scientific studies highlight its medicinal, biofertilizing, and metal-absorbing potential. Drawing on contemporary histories of the region’s industrial past, walks within the national park, and on the work of pteridologists, state forest officers, and entrepreneur residents, the paper examines the ‘invasive’ bracken fern as a vector form. The fern’s spatial dispersal, its proliferating tendency, and biophysical properties, the paper argues, not only require constant human efforts in managing its spread, but also provokes new conceptions of biodiversity as mobile and mutable. In doing so, I reflect on the challenges of building equitable multispecies futures in and around such ‘hotspots’.

Perpetual Motion Machine *Cameron Hu*

Of a transcontinental railroad carved through Western Texas in the later nineteenth century, a congressman complained that "we are letting a bird loose that we cannot catch anymore." He meant that in endowing the railroad's corporation with immortal legal life, the settler state had set in motion a quasi-autonomous agency whose trajectory was now beyond political control, possessed of independent drives and tendencies that caused it to steam beyond the finite political aspirations that had justified its creation. By the twenty-first century, the railroad "became" one of the world's largest and most destructive petroleum enterprises. In this paper, that series of mutations by which the one became the other describes the vector of a legal, political, and technoscientific agency loosed all at once from its prior limits: the business corporation chartered for immortality, set in plausibly permanent erratic motion, not only moving through historical time but increasingly producing historicity itself as it spreads out continuously.

Session Organizer:

Chloe Ahmann, Cornell University

Chair:

Jorge Benavides-Rawson, George Washington University

Discussant:

Jerry Zee, Princeton University

326. Biometrics on the Move - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Biometric practices have moved around the world through colonial and postcolonial contexts, transnational exchange, and private sector developments. They have become central to a variety of public and private infrastructures. Often, biometric technologies and data are not built from scratch, rather they are reformulated and repurposed to fit new times, places, and contexts. Automated face and fingerprint identification on smartphones, and biometric data in ID cards, are underwritten by similar methods of body measurement developed by 19th and 20th century eugenics, anthropology, statistics, and criminology researchers. States have appropriated biometric databases as digital platforms, which often serve as foundations upon which other infrastructures are organized. Biometric systems have been used, and reused, for purposes ranging from the delivery of government services to policing, from tracking refugees to COVID-19 mitigation efforts. This open track invites submissions that address the movement of biometric practices, and their social consequences. Panelists will explore not only how biometric techniques constitute emerging forms of identity governance, but also how they move across time and place, reorganize existing practices, and produce new kinds of infrastructures. Even in new contexts, biometric systems carry the biases and intentions of prior ones. These systems can fail, and present asymmetrical benefits and harms that reinforce inequalities related to race, gender, class, age, and disability. These systems also shape the lived experiences of citizenship, migration, surveillance, and access to services. This panel welcomes papers that leverage STS concepts and methods to probe the trajectories, implementations, and implications of biometrics on the move.

Participants:

The Datafication of Refugee Bodies: The Inscription of Power through Biometric Technologies *Mishall Ahmed*, York University, Canada

Biometric technologies have become one of the primary means of reading, measuring, and codifying refugee bodies (Jacobsen. 2015; Glouftsiou and Scheel. 2020). While there are instances of emancipatory digital technologies with reference to the use of information and communication technologies (ICT's) by refugees, scholars warn that biometric technologies and its subsequent reliance on physiological data have grave implications in terms of the further entrenching of power asymmetries and inequalities experienced by refugees (Madinou. 2019; Nedelcu and Soysuren. 2020). The social and political processes of differentiation that shape and inform new and emerging border technologies, the bodies of data, and the

datafied bodies they produce then come into effect as racialized inscriptions power on the body (Vukov.2016). Central here is the process of racialization inherent to the functions and applications of pre-emptive biometric border technologies, as illustrated through the highly racialized and differential targeting, engagement, and surveillance of marginalized communities in the post 9/11 era (Magnet. 2011). This paper seeks to examine what the incorporation of corporeal schemas of the body into the analysis of biometric technologies and its use on refugees means for Global North humanitarianism and its "others" (Fanon; 1952; Pedersen and Haioty. 2019; Amster. 2015). I argue that by incorporating the corporeal schemas of the body into our analysis of biometric technologies and algorithmic forms of surveillance, we are able to map the inscription of power onto refugee bodies and shed light on the larger project of racialization as enacted through biometric border technologies and differential surveillance.

Automated Speech Analysis In Asylum Procedures In Conflict With Fundamental Rights *Marla Meilinger*, University of Graz

In asylum procedures it is particularly important to identify a person's exact country and region of origin to determine the worthiness of protection and hence the refugee status. For this purpose, the German Federal Office for Migration and Refugees (Bamf) is currently developing a speech analysis tool for Arabic dialects using voice biometrics. The software is expected to recognise the speaker's accent and determine where he or she comes from. The German and Austrian Governments intend to rely on tools like the above mentioned in the asylum procedure. The constitutional admissibility is unclear since wrong decisions in asylum procedures may have life-threatening consequences. The software also faces technical problems: According to the Bamf, at least 20% of the results are false. That is not surprising: During their flight, refugees often live in different countries for several months and get in contact with many different languages. Every contact influences and changes their own language and dialect, which may make the use of the dialect recognition tool obsolete. This contribution will examine if using the tool with such a high level of inaccuracy violates fundamental rights. If authorities based their asylum decisions on a (false) result of the tool, the ruling may violate the fundamental rights to asylum (Art 18 Charter of Fundamental Rights), to a good administration (Art 41 Charter of Fundamental Rights), to respect for private and family life (Art 8 European Convention of Human Rights) and to a fair trial (Art 6 European Convention of Human Rights).

'Crisis', Control, and Crimmigration: Biometric Surveillance in the Policing of Migration *Nina Amelung; Matthias Wienroth*, Northumbria University

Automated facial recognition and advanced forensic DNA analyses are becoming dominant technological surveillance means for 'crimmigration' control. 'Crimmigration' describes the increasing criminalisation of migration based on the perceived 'crisis' of mass migration and its negative impact on national stability and welfare, materialising in overlapping crime and migration control regimes. In this paper we analyse policing of migration through biometric technologies as the reproduction of social practice of security. We bring together Elizabeth Shove's notion of social practice with Radin and Kowal's concept of ethical regimes. Ethical regimes consist of bureaucratic structures, systems, interpersonal relationships and values that legitimise the use of biomaterial and data. This analytical synthesis supports us in exploring how biometric technologies deployed in the policing of crime circulate into the policing of migration: (1) Technologies as materials (audio-visual recordings, DNA, fingerprints, analysis kits, software etc.) are inscribed with assumptions about validating identity and suspicion. (2) Forensic competence can move in abstracted forms of expertise independent of the context and ethics of application, creating challenges for technology deployment. (3) Biometric

technologies, often taken for granted as reliable, useful and accurate policing tools, travel from crime into migration with meanings which construct criminal suspicion of migrants. In order to evidence the complexity and difficulty of achieving accountability and responsibility for the ethical governance of biometric technologies in policing, we trace (i) how goals, risks, benefits and values of biometric surveillance technologies are framed, and (ii) how the legitimacy of their deployment in policing of migration is constructed and negotiated.

The technopolitics of Smart Borders in EU: From biometrics to biomarkers of deceit. *Vasilis Argyriou; Aristotelis (Aristotle) Tympas, National and Kapodistrian University of Athens*

The ongoing digitalization/smartification of the EU borders relies highly on biometric identifiers and data collecting techniques that are basic parts of a large scale IT infrastructure, which relies on the interoperability of different systems for the purpose of identifying and controlling mobility and migration movements across the EU. The “Smart Borders” project has recently moved on to the implementation process, while other parallel projects, like iBorderCtrl, are advanced by promising that collection of data “will move beyond beyond biometrics and on to biomarkers of deceit” (European Commission, 2018). The aim for both the projects was to facilitate the work of border guards in spotting illegal immigrants, and so contribute to the prevention of crime and terrorism, as well as to facilitate border procedures for bona fide and law-abiding travellers (The Project | iBorderCtrl, n.d.). Test pilots for both the projects were conducted in specific “high risk” areas/countries, like Greece, claiming to bring together many state of the art technologies, both hardware and software. These range from biometric verification, automated detection through biomarkers of deceit, document authentication and risk assessment. Although the iBorderCtrl project was rejected due to many legal and ethical concerns, the test pilots may serve as indicative for the broader effort to shape the technological future of EU mobility towards certain ends. This “strategic practice of designing or using technology to constitute, embody or enact political goals” (Hecht, 2009:19) appears in the technical proposals of the smart borders system, on the role and impact of the agents and the stakeholders that are related with the project and the overall process of shaping European identity. The presentation will focus on the connections between biometric identification techniques such as fingerprint enrollment and image identification with the ‘smartness mandate’ (Halpern, 2017), as well as with the digital mandate for border and migration management in EU.

Making biometric borders interoperable. A necessary political fiction? *Paul Trauttmansdorff, Department of Science and Technology Studies*

This contribution explores the sociotechnical trajectories and implications of making biometric databases interoperable in the border and migration regime of the European Union (EU). Interoperability has recently become a wide-spread buzzword, “enough to mean something and vague enough to work across multiple venues for multiple audiences” (Gillespie 2010, 349). It signals interconnectedness and the flexible use of data across multiple IT systems, building upon, and re-configuring, existing infrastructures and data practices. Recently adopted as a policy in the context of the EU border regime, interoperability redefines the purposes and scope of existing and future databases that collect, store and process identity data, fingerprints and facial images of migrants. Drawing on ethnographic observations and interviews, the paper aims to understand interoperability as an attempt of reinfrastructuring the border regime, i.e. shifting the meanings and practices of—as well as resistances against—biometric bordering in the EU. It particularly analyzes how interoperability has been translated from an initially contested and vague technical concept into a broader “necessary political fiction” (Ezrahi 2012). The study illustrates how interoperability not only reorganizes biometric techniques at the border but also

inscribes and normalizes normative assumptions of migrant identity and (un)certainly in EU bordering practices. Interoperability, then, serves as a window into the assemblage of actors, values, knowledges, and biometric technologies that participate in materializing the imaginary of digitally transforming borders. Finally, the paper discusses the role of “infrastructural shifts” in reinforcing the radically unequal distribution of mobility and rights in Europe.

Session Organizer:

Ranjit Pal Singh, Data & Society Research Institute

Chair:

Michelle Spektor, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

327. Caring Economies III

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Third installation of "Caring Economies," focusing on the role of digital platforms and services in caring economies.

Participants:

Caring in Crowds: Mass Digital Affects in Healthcare

Financing *Martha Lincoln, San Francisco State University*

Medical crowdfunding represents an emergent and morally charged form of a 'caring economy,' but the figure of the 'crowd' that animates this form of healthcare financing has gone largely unproblematized. This discussion draws on the influential sociological and economic imaginaries that have historically been used to characterize crowds and crowd behavior, asking how and why this ambivalent form of sociality is now imagined as a source of caring. While the crowd has long prompted moral panics in prior historic moments--anxiously imagined in terms of "the madness of crowds," "groupthink" and "the lonely crowd," and "mobbing" (c.f. Mackay 1841, Le Bon 1895, Canetti 1960, and Riesman et al. 1950)--crowds, or digital crowds, now contribute a significant and increasing share of the cost of health care in the United States. This paper takes stock of the shifting fortunes of the idea of "crowds," asking: What becomes of crowds in digital spaces? Is crowdfunding indeed a "crowd" phenomenon, or is it best understood as something else? Are the affective circulations impelling crowd behavior coopted or repurposed in crowdfunding exchanges? Finally, what does it mean to 'care in crowds,' and how does this behavior affect and shape its subjects?

Digital Infrastructures of Care: The Politics of Commodified Self-Care on Instagram *Schuyler Marquez, Arizona State University*

In recent years, transnational corporations, startup companies, and Instagram influencers alike have embraced the categories of self-care and wellness as capacious, innovative, and generative concepts for the promotion of commodified experiences and objects. By invoking self-care and wellness, various users seek to present and share commodified self-care as healing for the stressors and inequities endemic to what is couched as “traditional” modes of capitalism. This paper considers the ways in which users commodify and enact self-care and wellness on Instagram, a social media application that provides an infrastructure for users to exchange and circulate text and multimedia with other accounts that may be associated with individuals, corporations, or other institutions. Through digital ethnography and interviews with users on their use of the app, I examine how this digital arena is constituted as a seemingly frictionless locale for healing and renewal, despite the differences that users embody and struggle with away from the application. Drawing on theory and methods at the intersections of STS, economic anthropology, and media studies, I examine what concepts and practices of care are generated and afforded by this digital arena and consider what relations of power and subjectivities are obscured in these processes. By focusing on the ways this particular infrastructure is used to manage care and

good relations, I seek to further discussion on the implications that digital infrastructures, metrics, and algorithmic logics have for hegemonic medical practice and scientific authority and the effects these politics have for people traditionally marginalized by consumer capitalism.

The Limits of Care: building and maintaining software within a corporate environment *Paula Bialski, University of St. Gallen*

This paper focuses on the fluctuating care (and lack thereof) that a programmer experiences when building, maintaining and repairing software within a corporate software environment. Much like an artist cares for their craft, building commercial software can be a caring and creative endeavor. This creates a certain tension: on the one hand, programming is about care: an act of sociality between the programmer, their social world, and the sociotechnical system that is computational software. On the other hand, the corporate programmer builds their software within an economic order, basing their final decisions on the desires and needs of a customer. While being the experts on how a software system should be designed and how it should be cared for and maintained – they have to limit their care-for-their-software in order to meet certain economic demands and metrics of their managers and clients (known in corporate speak as “key performance indicators” or “KPI’s”). This begs the question: when do software developers decide to stop caring about their projects? Why do they care about some projects and not others? What happens when a project they care for suddenly gets thrown out for economic reasons? This paper draws on six months of situated fieldwork at a large Berlin-based corporate software company in order to reveal the dimensions of caring about how software is made and maintained, and the way this care is cut off, broken and limited due to certain corporate discourses and practices.

UberTherapy & Therapeutic Tinder: working in the therapy factory *Elizabeth Cotton, Cardiff Metropolitan University*

The proposal explored is that an ‘uberization’ is taking place in the UK’s mental health sector as a result of the strategic downgrading of services and jobs, through the introduction of the UK’s Increased Access for Psychological Therapies (IAPT) programme. The IAPT model is a short term manualized and increasingly digitalised cognitive behavioural model that dominates the UK’s mental health sector. The sector has seen the co-option of mental health into the UK’s austerity programmes and benefit sanctions with an emerging landscape of psycho-compulsion, sanctions and precarity for both practitioners and service users. This uberization represents an industrialisation of therapeutic work and a move towards ‘command & control’ performance management systems, online surveillance, and the gaming of performance data. With digital providers capitalising on the reorganisation of therapeutic work under Covid-19 online platforms offering therapeutic labour and AI and automation, clustered in diagnosis, monitoring and signposting in services are now mainstream, raising ethical concerns about the use of this data to feed into austerity programmes. Further, we will explore the question about the impact of ‘e-therapy’ on the therapeutic alliance in this policy climate. This uberized landscape opens up issues of resistance and solidarity and what the organising challenges are ahead for the progressive self-organised groups that are now emerging. This presentation will make use of surveys and interviews with mental health workers from 2017-2020 and experiences of mental health activism through survivingwork.org and thefutureoftherapy.org

Session Organizer:

Martha Lincoln, San Francisco State University

Discussant:

Emily Martin, NYU Department of Anthropology

328. Emergent Orders in the Governance, Institutions and

Knowledge Economies of Genome Editing Technologies - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

In the wake of the rapid development of novel genome editing technologies for manipulating DNA, most notably the CRISPR-Cas9 system, a wide variety of actors are vying for influence and access over their governance, development and use. Scientists, biohackers, patients, regulators, bioethicists, disability justice advocates, venture capitalists, biopharma and agriculture firms, among others, are contributing to and contesting the development of institutions for governing these biotechnologies. Key to these dynamics are the discourses, processes and practices through which existing scientific, social, political, economic and ethical orders are disrupted, co-produced, and stabilized to form emergent orders, and how and why some possibilities are opened while others are constrained. This paper session invites research that examines and explores the intertwined development of genome editing technologies and social institutions from diverse perspectives and contexts, and across different applications (e.g. agriculture; health and biomedicine; environmental management and gene drives). What discourses, processes, practices and norms are important for governing these novel biotechnologies? How is increased access to and expanded use of these biotechnologies reconfiguring existing social and institutional orders, and leading to new ones? How can we imagine and enact more democratic forms of engagement with and governance of novel biotechnologies? Overall, we are interested in developing a comparative and critical picture of the emergence of new social orders as the ability to modify DNA becomes commonplace, and in doing so, identify sites where existing inequalities or asymmetries of power are reproduced and can be addressed.

Participants:

Sociotechnical Imaginaries of Capacity: Observing and Explaining Regulatory Processes in Progress in Rapidly Changing Fields *Meghna Mukherjee; Konrad Posch, UC Berkeley*

“Sociotechnical imaginaries” (‘SIs,’ Jasanoff 2015) are not only crucial to the public’s conceptions of technologies, but also mutually co-constitute experts’ regulatory pathways. Regulators governing emerging technologies are challenged with anticipating innovation and its risks before these have been actualized. They must imagine possible futures shaped by technologies, social structures, and their goals to govern them effectively. This project compares how those SIs are constructed and used by regulators and stakeholders involved in two rapidly changing technologies: connected autonomous vehicles (CAVs) and CRISPR-Cas9. Through a comparative study of governance, we further the theoretical and analytical potential of SIs. Harnessing 33 in-depth interviews, we synthesize perspectives from experts and institutions who develop and regulate CRISPR-Cas9 (19 interviews) and CAVs (14). The analysis focuses on 3 key dimensions of regulation: (i) degree of novelty, (ii) risk perception, and (iii) decision-making authority. Subsequently, we propose a ‘Regulatory SI Continuum,’ capturing the configuration of SIs associated with each technology and implications on governance. The continuum is marked by ‘federated’ institutional structures and practices on one end, and ‘unitary’ on the other. While a federated regulatory SI (CAVs) is characterized by more contention around the 3 dimensions, a unitary SI (CRISPR-Cas9) represents more consensus. Where a technology lies on the continuum can, partly, determine how it is regulated. The continuum also establishes that SIs are far from static conceptions, but can co-exist and evolve alongside institutions and individuals. We invite researchers, regulators, and technologists to iterate this analytical tool, especially in its potential to inform governance.

Technoscientific Colonialist Paternalism, Science

Democratization and Human Genome Editing (HGE)

Regulation *Gabriela Arguedas, Universidad de Costa Rica*

The purpose of this paper is to explore some of the reasons why it is necessary and urgent to establish a Global Observatory on

Human Genome Editing (HGE), as proposed by Sheila Jasanoff and Benjamin Hulburt (Jasanoff and Hulburt, 2018) (Jasanoff, Hulburt and Saha, 2020). I'd like to contribute to the debate about the ethics and governance of HGE by exploring the power relations mirrored in and perpetuated in the complex social and political relationships that underlie and frame discussions of how HGE should be regulated. The current discussion about whether or not it is necessary to create a global and binding regulatory framework for HGE is deeply influenced by the technoscientific community working directly with biotechnologies such as CRISPR-Cas9, but the rest of society (especially in the Global South) have had almost no participation in those conversations. In order to assess these power relations and their impacts in this area, I have proposed the concept of "technoscientific colonialist paternalism." (Arguedas, 2020) To develop this analysis, this paper has three sections. First, I explain what constitutes "techno-scientific colonialist paternalism" and why it is harmful and should be confronted in the global discussion about the regulation of bio-tools like CRISPR-Cas9 to modify the human genome (specially germline editing). The second part is an overview of the limits of scientific self-regulation. In the final section I advocate for a Global Observatory that would be an agora in the democratization of the decision-making process that could lead to a global regulatory framework of HGE.

Democratizing Delphi: Towards More Inclusive Methodologies for Assessing Genome Editing Technologies *Koen Beumer, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University*

In this paper, we critically assess the Delphi study as a key institution for governing novel genome editing technologies. This is a method for priority-setting in which natural scientists are asked to identify and rank the positive societal implications of emerging technologies. This method is regularly applied to different biotechnologies and has been highly influential in steering R&D investments and policies (e.g. Juma & Yee-Cheong 2005; Cozzens et al. 2013; Beumer 2016). Our first aim is to draw upon STS literature to criticize the Delphi study as an institution for governing biotechnologies. The exclusive reliance on technical experts and the limited focus on positive societal implications ignores other relevant forms of expertise, including expertise on social, ethical, and political dimensions of technological change, as well as voices from communities that may be impacted by these technologies. Despite these shortcomings, however, time and time again the clear policy priorities provided by Delphi exercises prove to be very tempting for policymakers. We argue this makes the Delphi method a strategic point of intervention to steer genome editing towards more democratic directions. Our second aim is therefore to develop a more inclusive and democratic Delphi method and to apply this to genome editing. We propose this method should adhere to two principles: (1) diverse expertise (North and South, natural and social sciences, experts and publics), and (2) diverse impacts (benefits and detrimental impacts). This 'democratic Delphi' is a more democratic institution for governing genome editing technologies.

Undone Science And The Provision Of Public Global Goods At The International Potato Center *Sebastian Zarate, North Carolina State University*

The International Potato Center (IPC), member of the CGIAR network, is a Peruvian research center that provides improved genetic material to potato growing regions in developing countries. IPC's research seeks to be transformative in the sense that it provides public global goods to achieve United Nations Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). However, evidence in recent years shows that research on SDGs and transformative change remains marginal. This research aims to make sense of IPC's research priority assessments since the introduction of SDGs as core goals of CGIAR agenda. Undone science (Hess

2010) refers to unfunded, incomplete, or ignored research that becomes visible by non-scientists stakeholders. To explain the mismatches between research priorities and societal needs, this research aims to study the politics of priority setting and the potential alignments between IPC research and SDGs. Drawing on key insights of the New Political Sociology of Science (NPSS project), we are interested in how networks bridge institutional domains (science, policy, and international development) and influence IPC research agenda and practices. Does CGIAR focus on SDGs achievement hinder IPC's capacity to include broader or novel societal needs? Do CGIAR institutional dynamics and IPC's networks configurations hinder the provision of public global goods? How much science gets undone in the process and why? Why and how research priorities shift and who plays a center role in decision making?

National Scientific Capital and Biomedical Research in Contemporary China *Larry Au, Columbia University*

While science is global in rhetoric and aspiration, scientific work, its infrastructures, and funding is largely organized along national lines. In this paper, I draw on field theory (Bourdieu 1975) and studies of global fields (Buchholz 2016; Go and Krause 2016) to consider the formation of global and national scientific fields. Specifically, I examine the role of global and national scientific capital in shaping the research agenda of scientists. I take the case of precision medicine in China to understand how political, economic, and social problems are refracted in this national scientific field, and shape formation of a specific national scientific capital. Drawing on observations of scientific conferences and interviews with biomedical researchers in China, I argue that different combinations of global and national scientific capital orient researchers towards different visions of precision medicine. On one hand, proponents of what I call Chinese Precision Medicine that are oriented towards global scientific capital seek to redirect existing efforts in precision medicine to address "Chinese diseases" that they consider to be understudied by researchers based in the United States and Europe. On the other hand, advocates of Precision Chinese Medicine who are oriented towards national scientific capital seek to use the tools of genomics and bioinformatics to unlock the "black box" of traditional Chinese medicine, believing that these new techniques can complement traditional methods of diagnosis. In tracing the tensions between these different capital accumulation strategies, I shed light on the struggle between China's desires for global scientific leadership and technonationalism.

Session Organizer:

Dan Santos, Monash University (Australia)

Chair:

Santiago J Molina, University of California Berkeley

329. Living in a Nuclear World: Post-Fukushima Reflections on Nuclear Politics and History

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

The 2011 Fukushima nuclear disaster has prompted much reflection and new research among scholars of nuclear technology, disasters, and technoscientific governance. This panel collectively explores the emergence and maintenance of the global nuclear order from the post-Fukushima vantage point and transnational perspectives. Nuclear technology has profoundly changed the world and shaped a variety of relationships – among nations, among science, technology and society, and between humanity and the natural world, for instance. It has been an instrument for national security, a marker of national sovereignty, a site of technological innovation and a promise of energy abundance; it has also threatened human existence and fostered global institutions and movements. In revisiting the post-WWII years, the panel's papers present new perspectives on nuclear history and politics by focusing on four interconnected themes – violence and survival; containment and contamination; presuming and ignoring; and memories and futures – and

their relationships and consequences. More specifically, they address various intersected mechanisms whereby we have come to live in this nuclear world: colonialist discursive strategies to legitimate unequal national access to nuclear weapons; legal justification for subjecting marginalized populations to harms of nuclear tests; creation and dissemination of international safety standards; a shift of nuclear waste management from technical solutions to dependence on “nature”; and different orders of time to engage with nuclear technology’s consequences. These papers are products of a multi-year, international and multidisciplinary collaboration, and the panel will also reflect on the relationships that emerged and facilitated intellectual exchange and exploration.

Participants:

The Nuclear Charter: Modernizing US Imperialism in Micronesia, 1942-1947 *Mary Mitchell, University of Toronto*

The paper traces how the US turned Micronesia into a territory with a new status, United Nations Strategic Trusteeship, which virtually allowed unfettered US military power. It argues that a new synthesis between the material affordances, raw physical force of air atomic power, and scientific ideas about governance of dependent peoples justified new formations of US imperialism in Micronesia, subjugating indigenous islanders to dependency and irreparable harms from nuclear tests.

Mobilizing Tropes of Gender, Race and Pathology, along with Worst-case Scenario Thinking, to Construct a Postcolonial Regime of World Order *John Krige, Georgia Institute of Technology*

The paper looks at how the US minimized the unprecedented violence made possible by nuclear weapons. In particular, in addition to policies based on the worst-case scenario thinking, the US also used discursive strategies to construct a system of “nuclear apartheid” that denies others access to nuclear weapons. By tracing how tropes of gender, pathology and race were mobilized in this, the paper highlights the fragile foundations of an international system whose legitimacy is based on colonial and post-colonial assumptions.

“Dual Use” and the Conundrum of Control: The International Atomic Energy Agency and Nuclear Regulation through Standardization *Angela Creager, Princeton University; Maria Rentetzi, Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nuernberg*

The paper scrutinizes the IAEA’s early effort to both promote and monitor the development of atomic energy in its member states as its technical-cum-political enterprise: a “tool for governing the world.” Notably, by establishing and disseminating radiological safety standards as well as safeguarding the atom, the agency came to embody a new regulatory presence that used technical standards to shape the dissemination of technologies, materials, and practices. We argue that the ‘dual use’ of atomic energy necessitated a different regime of geopolitical control than other postwar technologies.

Governing Nuclear Waste by Nature and Technology *Tania Navarro Rodriguez, CERMES3 INSERM U988*

The paper takes on the governance of ever-growing nuclear waste at the transnational level. Analyzing past and present decisions regarding radioactive waste management, it interrogates how experts and decision-makers saw solutions in a partnership between nature and technology, and how they came to characterize waste problem as geological and environmental. I argue that this framing contributed to the transformation of the waste challenge from a domain of human action into an issue of nature.

Framing a Nuclear Order of Time *Bernadette Bensaude Vincent, Université Paris 1-Panthéon-Sorbonne*

The paper challenges the dominant view that Hiroshima and Nagasaki have undermined the modern techno-optimist view of

progress by raising the fear of an imminent end of humanity. Highlighting visions of a utopian future with free and abundant energy that also followed the bombings, the paper argues that both visions were rooted in the modern order of time, with its time-arrow oriented toward a future that makes sense of the present. And decades of tensions and contradictions between these visions did not deeply alter the modern view of humans as masters of nature. I argue that it was the environmental movement in the 1970s and 1980s that reconfigured the nuclear order of time, with the debate on nuclear winter shifting the public attention to the long-term impacts of nuclear radiation on the planet.

Session Organizer:

Kyoko Sato, Stanford University

Chair:

Soraya Boudia, University of Paris CERMES3

Discussant:

Scott Knowles, KAIST (Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology)

330. Quantum Technologies as Technological Promise: Toward an Uncertain Future - I: History, Philosophy, and Politics of Quantum Technologies

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Participants:

Anti-Democratic Politics in Quantum Technology *Emma McKay, McGill University*

There is quantum tech with material politics that make relational democratic decision-making difficult. For instance, as expensive, cryogenically cooled machines, quantum computers will likely always be few and far between, controlled by wealthy corporations and military labs. On the other hand, narratives about the democratization of quantum tech continue to grow; this frame puts access to (corporate-owned) technology at the centre of ethical & political questions in the field. The focus of this talk will be analysing the contrast between this narrative and the socio-material arrangements of specific quantum tech. I’ll start with a brief review of these democratization and access narratives, highlighting their usage in quantum ethics discourse. Then, following Winner (1980), I’ll turn to the technologies and their enmeshed social structures. I will focus on optimization, a near-term usage of quantum tech that relies on quantum annealers. The function and promise of optimization is to help production lines, airlines, and hedge funds make more profit faster, serving capitalist relations above all. My main source of data will be presentations made by companies interested in optimization from the 2020 Quantum 2 Business conference, supplemented with research papers on quantum optimization. This study on the politics of quantum technoscience points out durable contradictions between liberatory politics and ethics and material tech. It aims to contribute to work within and around STS in refusing technoscience which does not serve liberatory political structures. Winner, L. (1980). Do artifacts have politics? *Daedalus*, 109(1):121–136.

Closure of interpretational questions on quantum theory *Pieter Vermaas, Delft University of Technology*

Title Edit Title Closure of interpretational questions on quantum theory Abstract Edit Abstract The emergence of quantum technology is from a technological point of view an impressive development: starting in physics and logic, it went via computer science and engineering, to now companies till it will reach its projected endpoint of retail outlets. From a sociologically point of view this development is one in which quantum theory is becoming a topic for an increasing number of stakeholder groups. Being initially a topic confined to physics and philosophy, it is now one that involves computer scientists,

electrical engineers and beyond that, e.g., funding agencies, business developers and venture capitalists. Assuming quantum technology will be a success, even more groups become involved as, say, educators for teaching the needed new quantum technologists, and policy makers for anticipating the economical and military uses. In this contribution I will explore with the SCOT framework by Pinch and Bijker how this scaling of the number of stakeholder groups can affect the traditional question of interpretation in quantum physics. Academic debates on this question of how physical reality looks like if quantum theory is true, could in the last century not be settled among physicists and philosophers. With the emergence of new groups this question may find closure in the sense of SCOT. The interpretation of quantum theory is hardly surfacing in presentations of quantum technologies, and attempts at explaining concepts such as superposition and entanglement are more aimed at making these concept colloquial than enigmatic. Extrapolating this development, the question of interpretation in quantum physics may become settled by engineers and educators.

Quantum Nationalisms and Internationalisms *Susannah Glickman, Columbia University*

The internationalization of scientific research—a process sponsored by the US government for cynical reasons during the Cold War—became more pronounced after the end of the Cold War. Constant circulation around the globe became increasingly necessary for scientists in establishing and maintaining coherent fields of study. At the same time, the technologies involved have become more central to different articulations of technoscientific nationalisms and claims to hegemony. China, for example, seems in part to be staking its emergence as a great power on its emergence as a technoscientific leader. Quantum technologies constitute one of the major technologies pursued with the aim of demonstrating China's technoscientific modernity. The end of the Cold War sent institutions built for the Cold War framework scrambling to define their purpose, and the meaning of global competition and power. Technoscience as a result became one of the mediums for performing hegemony. Building on my fieldwork internationally on the subject of quantum computing and information with more than 60 researchers and other important figures from across academia, government and industry in the US, Japan, the EU, China, the United Kingdom, Singapore, and Israel, as well as Cold War histories of the origins of international science in the American model, this paper will track and explain these different developments and offer an account of what these developments mean for post Cold War scientific ecosystems. Quantum computing and information provides a neat case study as its development coincided with the processes this paper seeks to describe.

Session Organizer:

Susannah Glickman, Columbia University

Discussant:

Zeki Can Seskir, Middle East Technical University

331. Re-thinking And Experimenting With Participatory Research Practices And Design Through The Speculative And Ontological Turn - II: Methods and Practices

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Experimenting with worlds *Peter Danholt, Aarhus University*

At the heart of many approaches in the fields of STS, design and participatory research are mutual engagement and involvement with others. Follow the actors, mutual learning, ecologies of practice are some of the famous credos of this concern. Engagement and participation arguably presume some sort of shared ontology or worlds with those that we engage with and undoubtedly, we do share ontologies. But which ontologies or worlds do we in fact share or how might we explore and

experiment with what is shared and what is not? Inspired by recent work in STS and social anthropology and specifically and among others the work of Eduardo Viveiros de Castro, Marilyn Strathern, Jon Bialecki and Bruno Latour, I wish to discuss how we can think and practice participation and engagement as 'experimenting with worlds'. For instance, inspired by de Castro and his amerindian ontology, we could propose that instead of researchers and participants having different practices, but share what 'technology', 'workshop' and 'post-it' is, we might inversely propose that we share the same practice, namely 'work to accomplish something', but what 'technology', 'workshop' and 'post-it' is, are entirely different things for the parties involved.

Exploring the Temporalities of a Tandem in the Jungle *Liam Healy, Goldsmiths, University of London*

This paper explores temporality in design research by examining a tandem bicycle research device that was deployed in the Calais 'Jungle' refugee camp between 2016 and 2019. I examine a set of stories made in the field to explore the multiple relationships and ontologies that the tandem bicycle participates in (and produces). I first examine the relationship between agency, waiting and boredom in the camp, and problematise the different (and sometime shared) experiences between researchers, displaced people and police that the bike alerts me to. I then examine the different possibilities and temporalities that the device was able to enact by momentarily escaping the researcher's control. I argue that developing ways to practice participatory forms of speculative design — what I call a-firmative speculation — requires a re-thinking of temporality to the linear conceptions of time (like past, present and future) prevalent in design discourses and practices. To problematize these, I draw on Elaine Gan et al.'s assertion that we should be careful not to think of ladders as the only image of time (2017: G9), but develop alternative ways of conceiving of the present and so-called futures. In doing so I draw a distinction between a conception of care, that on the one hand is concerned with protecting and closing down possibilities, and on the other, a speculative version concerned with bringing about new possibilities and consequences.

The measure of things and the things of measurement:

Metrology, Speculation and Design *Mike Michael, University of Exeter*

It is suggested that the relation between multinaturalism and multiculturalism can be understood to be variably configured. Haraway's version of naturecultures is particularly helpful in that it enables the exploration of the exigencies that underpin the manifestation of multiple naturecultures in their specificity. This paper explores the critical and speculative dimensions of the specificity of naturecultures through the dramatised contrast between different forms of metrology, roughly divided into lay and expert versions. While measurement of particular manifestations of 'nature' (for example, distance, space, mass) is typically mediated through various expert bodies, these enter a lay world of everyday conceptions of practical measures. Not unusually, designers can mediate between these worlds through the practices of visualization, for instance. By contrast, on the one hand, it is proposed that the interplay of multinaturalism and multiculturalism can be critically examined (e.g. how technically extended expert bodies are bound up with lay skepticism or irony; practical lay measures are subject to expert measures of knowledge deficits). On the other hand, design is directed toward the speculative 'concatenation' of different naturecultures which combine, amongst other things, affects, ideas, technologies, institutions and bodies into novel units of measurement that inventively re-problematise the relation between multinaturalism and multiculturalism.

Trajectories of Engagement: Translational Challenges of Involving End-Users in the Co-Design of AI-based Affective Technologies *Rossio Motta-Ochoa, McGill University;*

Natalia Incio-Serra, McGill University; Dannie Fu, McGill University; Stefanie Blain-Moraes, McGill University

Participatory design or co-design is considered an effective approach to engage end-users of technologies in all stages of the design process, and to create a space of mutual learning and collaboration. Technologies designed using a participatory approach are more likely to be fair, transparent, inclusive and empowering of end-users. However, artificial intelligence (AI)-based affective technologies – systems and devices that can recognize, process and human emotions – demand computational and emotional knowledge from end users, often limiting their involvement in the participatory design. In this paper, we reflect on the participatory design process of biomusic – a novel affective technology that translates emotion-related features of a user’s physiological signals into real-time sonic/musical outputs. Using ethnographic methods (participant observation, informal interviews and semi-structured interviews), we have traced how six dyads of biomusic co-designers, each comprised of an individual with limited communicative abilities and his/her main caregiver, interacted with biomusic. We identify trajectories of engagement with the participatory design of biomusic and characterize these trajectories through challenges that our co-designers encountered and how they responded to them. The main challenge was a misunderstanding of the technologically mediated translations (Latour, 1998; Mol, & Law, 1994; Mol, 2002) involved in biomusic, and how the co-designers handled this challenge influenced the course of their trajectories of engagement with the co-design process. Finally, we reflect on how participatory design could help control the equivocations (Viveiros de Castro, 2004) involved in the translations that constitute AI-based affective technologies and has the potential to support equitable AI systems that empower end-users.

Co-Speculating Business Sustainability across Ontological Difference *Michael Hockenhuil, IT University of Copenhagen*

This paper explores the potentials of co-speculation for creating effective data infrastructures to address business sustainability. It is based on a developing research project in Denmark to design, create and populate a database which will track corporate sustainability efforts. The paper provides an initial analysis of sustainability efforts in the Danish corporate sector, informed by the perspectives of the ontological turn, to suggest that it’s understanding of climate change differs ontologically from that of many other actors in the climate field (such as researchers, activists, politicians, etc). The paper argues that given the importance of corporations in contributing to the ongoing climate crises, creating a successful data infrastructure detailing their sustainability efforts is crucial to efforts to research their (lack of) transition and create popular pressure on them to increase their pace, yet requires their participation to be most effective. To bridge the ontological difference between actors and facilitate such participation, the paper suggests experimentation with co-speculation. Concretely, the paper suggests and explores the creation of several workshops to facilitate the co-speculative design of the data infrastructure itself, as a means to turn business sustainability into a matter of concern shared by different kinds of actors. Co-speculation here means, following Donna Haraway, engaging materially in speculative fabulation of the concrete form, content, metrics and means of access of the proposed data infrastructure itself. It also means the creation of relations between actors through collaborative speculation on different possibilities and futures.

Session Organizer:

Peter Danholt, Aarhus University

332. Technology, Aesthetics, and the Body II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

People are increasingly tasked with both the aesthetic and scientific

management and optimization of their bodies. For women and non-binary people, in particular, “health” and “beauty” are not simply individual achievements, but comprise the terrain in which battles over the “fitness of the race and the nation” have been played out (Strings 2019:194). Technologies from X-ray machines to Fitbits are mobilized in these fights. STS has analyzed how gender and racial ideologies are embedded within such technologies. This panel draws attention to technologies of the body with a particular eye toward aesthetics. How does the body become articulated, legible, and fortified through the use of technology? We are especially interested in everyday, mundane objects that have often not been analyzed as technologies, such as cosmetics, clothing, and accessories. Technologies of embodiment like cosmetics have been dismissed as commodities or frivolities. But subjects use them to resist subordination and to express themselves in ways that can subvert oppression at personal and structural scales. We invite submissions of papers about technologies of embodiment, enhancement and adornment, especially on the following subjects: -The disruption of the binary between natural and artificial -The enforcement of the gender binary, heteronormativity, and transmisogyny -The construction or disruption of racial and colonial formations -The political economy of makeup -Fashion -Beauty gurus and social media influencers -Cosmetic surgery -DIY body and “bio” hacking

Participants:

AI Enabled Fashion Assistants and the Politics of Embodied Interactions *Nassim Parvin, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Whether it is a veil or an afro, a hoodie or drag, the weight and significance of fashion is all too familiar—especially to those at the margins. There is indeed a double bind: those at the margins of society are scrutinized more for what they wear—their life and death, even, might depend on it. As a result they are more likely to be hyper aware about their bodies inclusive of what they could and should wear. Yet, the same attentiveness is viewed as a mark of inherent inferiority given the dominant framing of fashion as frivolous and unworthy of intellectual attention. Relatedly, compared to those applications of artificial intelligence and big data that pose a direct threat to lives and livelihoods such as drones, self-driving cars, or smart policing, digital fashion assistants may seem like innocuous gadgets that have not received much scholarly attention. Yet, as I will argue in this presentation, such technologies are poised to profoundly impact our interpersonal and collective interactions. Indeed, the introduction of digital fashion assistants and other beauty apps surfaces ethical and political issues that may have been invisible otherwise, in this case no less than the centrality of our bodies in constitution of our social and political relations. The specificity of the domain is also productive for seeing this category of technology anew, illuminating its taken-for-granted premises and lofty promises with implications for other areas of the application of artificial intelligence.

Uncanny Techno-Aesthetics : “Plastic Surgery Monsters” or Gangnam Beauty in the 21st century’s Korea *So Yeon Leem, Sookmyung Women’s University*

South Korea has gone through extreme transformations due to rapid development and Westernization since 1960s. Gangnam as the southern part of Seoul, the capital city of South Korea, has been a symbol of the miraculous economic growth and modern lifestyle, including modern beauty-making. Since the early 2000s, Gangnam has had a domestic and international reputation as “plastic surgery special district” and plastic surgery recipients has been identified as “Gangnam beauty.” Gangnam beauty has become a symbol of Korean modern beauty which is now widespread into other Asian societies through medical and cultural goods. Korean bodies with technological intervention seem to embody aesthetics that appeal globally. However, not all Gangnam beauty is beautiful. Some of them make people feel disgusted or creepy. They are the ones (mainly women) who are called “plastic surgery monsters”. These monsters usually have excessively large eyes, high noses, and pointed jaws all of which was created by a series of plastic surgery. Some say that they

have failed transforming into a white woman's face and others see them too frivolous to achieve a natural beauty. To me, they are like Orlan, a French performance artist who has a monstrous face against patriarchal beauty norms through plastic surgery. Plastic surgery monster's beauty does not reflect but diffract male-dominant aesthetics as Orlan's performance does. However, their diffraction is not intentional: those monster women transgress patriarchal beauty norms while embodying it in the most sincere ways. They are like humanoid robots trying to resemble humans: they unintentionally fall into the uncanny valley. This study attempts to analyze plastic surgery monsters with a Japanese roboticist Masahiro Mori's famous hypothesis, the Uncanny Valley theory. Based on resources gathered from cultural representations and interviews along with theoretical investigation, I will draw technological, aesthetic, and political implications of Korean plastic surgery monsters. In this study, what is techno-aesthetically uncanny is not only the surgically modified beauty of Korean women at present but also the Westernized Korean nation from the past and the technologically enhanced humans in future.

Skinship: Relationality and Skin Microbiopolitics *Heather Mellquist Lehto, Arizona State University*

The skin is one of the most important thresholds in human life, constituting a boundary of one's body as well as a medium for relation with others. Yet, there is no universal, trans-historical understanding of the skin. Rather, how people relate to and through their skin is informed by conceptions of race and gender, public health projects, scientific research, religious traditions, and cosmetics industries. This presentation draws on ethnographic research within the K-beauty cosmetics industry, with research scientists, and with public health officials in South Korea and the United States to analyze the recent research and product development related to the skin microbiome. The increasing use of prebiotic, probiotic, and postbiotic skin treatments cultivates not only the skin's materiality, but also a distinctive awareness of one's interdependence with bacterial fermentation processes, as well as the broader, environmental conditions necessary to maintain the skin as a complex ecosystem. Korean beauty industries, in particular, use this interest in the microbiome to create new social and economic ties internationally by capitalizing on the country's long-held fermentation practices. This ethnographic research traces how skin microbiome research has shifted how dermatologists, cosmetics developers, and skincare users understand the materiality of the skin. Inspired by the Korean/Japanese term "skinship" [스킨십] and Heather Paxson's "microbiopolitics," I give particular attention to the sociopolitical implications of such scientific knowledge and skincare practices, showing how shifting conceptions of the skin work to reconfigure social and ecological relations.

Session Organizer:

Alka Menon, Yale University

Chair:

Alka Menon, Yale University

333. After Normal: Post-Normal Living

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

In retrospect, the 20th century may have been the Century of the Normal. The normal and its variations—the normate, the normative, the norm, and normality—have guided scholarly attention to institutions, processes of subjectivity, categories of personhood, and everyday interactions. As a set of heuristics, the normal and its variations helped to point attention toward racist, ableist, sexist, and homophobic biases in medical and scientific practice, in governance, in institutional arrangements, and throughout society—in the North Atlantic and elsewhere. But what happens after the normal? If the early 21st century has demonstrated anything, it is that the normal is not what it used to be as a heuristic or set of practices. Maybe this is the downstream effect of two decades of debate around postmodernism,

liquid modernity, and performative drag; maybe this is a function of norm-breaking political movements, nationally and globally. Maybe the erosion of the normal is an effect of the waves of intersectional and identity critiques that dislodged cisgendered, able-bodied, heterosexual, middle class whiteness from its foundational basis as the normal. Or maybe it is the effect of scholarly attention to already existing communities refusing or practicing normality according to their own logics. Scholars working at the intersections of science and technology studies, critical race theory, disability studies, and within feminist and anti-colonial frameworks have been critical here. Entering into 2021, it is fair to say that we are "after normal." But where does that leave us? The normal still pervades medicine, science, and everyday life. What tools have science and technology scholars uncovered for articulating a move away from the normal and its legacies? How might we—individually and collectively—reconceptualize the basis of normalcy from insights provided by ethnographic, archival, and other empirical work that exposes the fissures in the normal and its powers.

Participants:

What comes after cochlear implantation and habilitation?: From hoping for to expecting normally sensing children *Michele Friedner, The University Of Chicago*

While scholars have attended to the ways that disability has become a new normal and is increasingly present as a category and experience in public spheres, this talk argues that technologies such as cochlear implants and accompanying therapeutics make it possible for children to become "normal." Parents come to expect, rather than hope, that interventions will work. An analysis of habilitating children with cochlear implants in India—and habilitation as a process and practice in general—foregrounds the ways that potentiality attaches to certain kinds of bodyminds because of the presumed existence of malleability. Certain bodyminds are seen as possessing more potential for habilitation because they are malleable. Just as scholars have critically attended to rehabilitation, habilitation too is an important process of activating what is perceived to be latent and has future-oriented stakes. However, while normality—or normal hearing—might be attainable, it needs to be maintained through on-going work. And in maintaining normality, other possibilities for sensing, communicating, and engaging are backgrounded, ignored, and/or contracted. But when is normal attained and when can a successful outcome be claimed? If a child is, for example, at grade level in terms of vocabulary and their audiograms are "normal," does that mean that habilitation processes are over? If rehabilitation is marked by temporal disjunctions and ostensibly return and restoration, habilitation is an entirely future-oriented endeavor. But what happens when the future becomes the present? What then, comes, after normal?

Syndemic Normality: COVID-19, Type 2 Diabetes, and Climate Change *James Doucet-Battle, University of California, Santa Cruz*

The COVID-19 pandemic has acquainted many people globally with the sedentary realities of quarantine and (self-imposed) shelter-in-place restrictions. These restrictions, combined with climate change induced fires and deep freezes across the US, has raised concerns about a decrease in physical activity and an increase in weight gain, what some have called "the quarantine fifteen." For diabetics (Types 1 and 2), physical activity constitutes a vital component in maintaining overall health. Moreover, obesity and diabetes disproportionately affect underserved racial and ethnic minority populations and serve as preconditions with co-morbidities that increase COVID-19 susceptibility - a constellation of pandemic risks and illnesses Singer (1997) called a syndemic. This paper directs its focus through the lens of diabetes to examine the ways people with diabetes have begun to adjust to living with the illness during the pandemic, and how the pandemic has changed clinician diabetes treatment. Drawing also from Canguilhem (2012), we ask: How has this novel syndemic normality affected public health

outreach, education and support of diabetes patients? And lastly in connection, what role has technology played in making therapeutic adjustments to COVID-19 and the climate change? Arguably, the obesity, Type 2 diabetes, and climate change syndemics preceded COVID-19 and will doubtless succeed it. What is not fully known are the ways that diabetes as a social form and item of analysis will take shape anew in the post-COVID-19 future.

After Zika: Habilitative Caring towards a New Normal *Kathryn Eliza Williamson, Washington University in St. Louis*

Beginning in 2015, Brazil witnessed the births of thousands of babies with neurological “abnormalities” linked to the Zika virus. The unprecedented nature of what is now known as congenital Zika syndrome (CZS) has engendered a great deal of uncertainty in the lives of those affected by the pandemic, both children and their caregivers. Parents know their multiply disabled children will never be “normal,” yet doctors and therapists are unable to tell them exactly what to expect of their children’s development. Uncertainty thus becomes a source of hope: if no one knows what awaits, anything might be possible. Based on ongoing ethnographic research with a group of families in Northeast Brazil begun in 2016, this paper explores how parents navigate the normal and the possible (or the possibly possible) in the care of small children diagnosed with CZS. I focus here on their investments—financial, temporal, energetic—in their children’s potential, and the habilitative imaginaries these investments draw upon. I show how the normal and the possible are made, materially and conceptually, through engagements with therapeutic technologies, and how the habilitative imaginaries they’re entangled with reflect the sociopolitical realities of contemporary Brazil. This paper invites conversation on caregiving and (re)habilitative technologies beyond and alongside “normal.”

Discussing normalcy: childhood stunting prevention in Guatemala *Luisa Madrigal Marroquin*

Guatemala has the highest rate of childhood stunting in Latin America and ranks sixth in the world. Stunting, which refers to linear stature (length/height) that is two standard deviations below what is defined as normal for a child, is associated with reduced brain development, which in turn is related to diminished learning capacity, poor school performance, predisposition to some communicable diseases, and reduced income in adult life. Besides being discussed as a health and developmental condition, the public discourse surrounding childhood stunting in Guatemala has racialized undertones. Maya children, part of the country’s indigenous majority, exhibit higher rates of stunting. Different public and private actors are involved in the prevention of childhood stunting. Along with nutrition and health interventions executed in the first thousand days of life, national efforts to prevent stunting emphasize educating on what the condition is and what are their consequences. An unexpected outcome of these efforts has been the way in which the condition is discussed among ordinary citizens. Based on fieldwork with corporate executives, public health officials, corporate philanthropy administrative and fieldworkers, and targeted beneficiaries of interventions to prevent stunting, this presentation examines how knowledge claims about childhood stunting, development, normalcy, and race are generated, disseminated and experienced by those living with the condition.

Rethinking entanglements of race, biology, and the body after the normal *Oliver Rollins, University of Washington; Jarmin Yeh, University of California, San Francisco*

Calls for a return to “normal” has permeated throughout local and national publics as the world continues to grapple with the devastating effects of the COVID-19 pandemic. However, the Black Lives Matter protests, in the wake of the murders of Breonna Taylor, George Floyd and countless others by law enforcement, brings the seemingly benign calls for a return to

normalcy into sharp contrast with the normative practices of racial inequity in the US. Unlike the “post-racial” imaginaries that were flaunted after the 2008 election of Barack Obama, the post- or after- effects of the BLM protests of summer 2020 have led to greater attention to the enduring legacies of racism. Interestingly, the science and biomedical fields, areas which have historically tried to stay “neutral” when it comes to race, are now also raising the alarm, although in a haphazard fashion, about their own inattention to the politics of race and need for new normal in science; an anti-racist science. If a new politic of difference is possible in science and biomedicine “after the normal,” what will (can) it look like? How might lessons from STS help anticipate, disrupt, and/or help sustain such a knowledge project? In this paper, we take “after the normal” as an empirical question to help elucidate the potentials for this new kind of biopolitics of difference. Drawing from post-colonial STS and cultural theory, we first interrogate the work of “after” or “post” in relation to normative modes of knowledge production about race difference. We then trace where and how aspects of the norm may be interrupted, displace, or replace to think more seriously about both ideological and material practices of race through a critique of the entangled relationships between race and embodiment in biomedical and technoscientific research. By thinking about the inscription of power on/through the body, the representation of (racial) identity, and the discursive production of knowledge/power we hope to elucidate better the processes through which notions of the norm, normalization, and the normative gradually reflect unequal ideological dispositions within and hierarchy of values of society (Canguilhem 1991). We conclude with a discussion about the potential for an antiracist science after the normal, and the possibilities and potential pitfalls of this theoretically new racial normal in science and technology.

Session Organizer:

Michele Friedner, The University Of Chicago

Discussant:

Matthew Wolf-Meyer, Binghamton University

334. Situating, transforming, and (de)centering Images of the Futures - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Our current realities are a mess to embrace: the current global pandemic and its disruptions in labor, education, and other socio-technical systems; the increasing political and ontological polarizations and the urgent action against a human-catalyzed climate emergence are challenged our notion of safety, certainty, and even the survival of life on earth (as the ongoing massive extinction, and other fateful events). Our cartesian imaginations in fiction, planning, modeling, anticipation, and foresight are being defied for the unknown, opening a public demand for new ecological, material, and inter-mutual relations around the globe. A source of these imaginations are images of the future. In 1961, Frederick Polak defined it as “images of the totally other, and they are revolutionary and radical in nature, or they are nothing at all”. Future studies have contributed to popularize these images, (Inayatullah, 2008; Zheltikova & Khokhlova, 2019), which are connected to the movements of decolonial anthropologies and designs (Tlostanova, 2017; Escobar, 2018; Schultz, 2018), as well offer powerful insight for the study of emergent socio-technical imaginaries (Jasanoff, 2015; Konrad & Böhle, 2019). This panel wants to set a conversation around the role of images of the future in STS, in particular projects and practices looking at local, topical, or systemic images. We hope to have contributions to understanding how to situate, expand, nuance, and (de)centered “images of the futures”, to produce alternative realities (like Afro-futurism or Solar-Punk), and to restore more-than-human balances from the unequal, unbalanced, and unfair relations across scales.

Participants:

Gene Technologies in the Anthropocene: Reasons to Promote and Resist Images of the Future *Sigfrid Kjeldaas, GenØk*

Centre for Biosafety

As humanity faces environmental problems of unprecedented scales in the Anthropocene, new gene technologies are frequently presented as instrumental in creating more sustainable futures. In line with this cultural imaginary, the Norwegian Biotechnology Advisory Board in 2017 proposed to revise Norwegian legislation on gene technology to accommodate the development and future use of new gene editing technologies. This paper uses the ensuing public debate as a case study of how images of the future are utilized in arguments for or against the use of gene technologies. It starts with the observation that many agricultural, environmental and research organizations show more restraint than developers of gene technology in presenting visions of the future. Highlighting the fate of concepts like sustainability, biodiversity and climate change adaptation in discourses of modernist control over the future, I compare the logic and metaphors of modernity to the metaphors of ecofeminist new materialist theories concerned with life (and death) in the Anthropocene. The aim is to explain what is at stake for agricultural, environmental and scientific organizations who resist modernity's imaginaries for the future, choosing instead to 'stay with the trouble' (Haraway 2016) of an entangled present shaped by the past. Findings are discussed in light of changing international trends in environmental governance over the past thirty years (Foster 2021; Stirling 2018). They highlight how resistance against visions of environmental management and control represents attempts to re-establish issues of democratic inclusion and an ethics of care left behind as environmental governance engaged with the Anthropocene.

Futures Images In Higher Education – Digital Future Workshops For Participatory Sustainability Transformation *Lisa Kinne, netzwerk n e.V.; Ludwig Weh, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*

To adapt to the current pandemic restricting physical interaction in higher education, the project 'Students create sustainable universities in Northrhine-Westphalia' (<https://www.netzwerk-n.org/info/macherinnen/#NRW>) by German NGO netzwerk n has developed an innovative digital program (<https://kurs.netzwerk-n.org/>) using transdisciplinary and transformative learning elements in Education for Sustainable Development (Wals 2006). Core objective of the eight-week massive open online course is to empower and connect student promoters for sustainable university transformation. Framed as transdisciplinary praxis research, the project aims to develop personal sustainability competences (Wiek et al. 2006, de Haan 2010); build transformative capacity; strengthen agency of local bottom-up communities (Masini 2006); employ normative and (self-)reflexive elements in multi-method applications; raise critical awareness for inequalities and accountability in global development (Andreotti 2006). Course content draws on sustainability theory, environmental psychology, futures studies and more. Learning methods encourage creation and discourse about alternative futures images of sustainable institutions, processes and education; human-nature-interaction and more-than-human futures. The integrated digital future workshop based on the original method (Jungk & Müllert 1987, Dator 1993) explores a novel approach to assess futures images individually and collectively in digital space. Videoconferences, instructive audiobooks, and interactive whiteboards are used for participatory exchange in this integrative, easy-access online format. We present for discussion the conceptual background and methodological premises used for design, implementation and scientific evaluation (Wiek & Iwaniec 2014) of digital future workshops as innovative method. Participants' structured critique, utopia envisioning and specific project development provide valuable insights into the use of futures images for higher education sustainability discourse and transformative action. Andreotti, V. (2006). Theory without practice is idle, practice without theory is blind: the potential contributions of

post-colonial theory to development education. *Development Education Journal*, 12(3), 7. Dator, J. (1993). From future workshops to envisioning alternative futures. *Futures Research Quarterly*, 9(3), 108-12. De Haan, G. (2010). The development of ESD-related competencies in supportive institutional frameworks. *International Review of Education*, 56(2), 315-328. Jungk, R., & Müllert, N. (1987). Future Workshops: How to create desirable futures. *Inst. for Social Inventions*. Masini, E. (2006). Rethinking futures studies. *Futures*, 38(10), 1158-1168. Wals, A.E.J. (2006). The end of ESD... the beginning of transformative learning. Emphasizing the 'E' in ESD. In: Cantell, M. (Ed.). *Proceedings of the Seminar on Education for Sustainable Development held in Helsinki, February 15, 2006*. Wiek, A., Withycombe, L., & Redman, C. L. (2011). Key competencies in sustainability: a reference framework for academic program development. *Sustainability science*, 6(2), 203-218. Wiek, A., & Iwaniec, D. (2014). Quality criteria for visions and visioning in sustainability science. *Sustainability Science*, 9(4), 497-512.

Care and Relational Practices for Alternative Future Imaginaries in Brazilian Public Education *PAULA LUDERITZ DE ALBUQUERQUE LENZ CESAR, PUC-Rio; Magda Pischetola, IT University Copenhagen*

The majority of Brazilian public schools are a context where poverty and social injustice become visible, as most of the students come from disadvantaged realities. Their future is at risk, due to a general lack of social mobility and exclusion from civil rights and minimal living conditions. This situation has worsened with the global pandemic emergence; giving attention to this topic has become even more urgent. This paper moves from the example of Brazilian public schools to investigate how a disowned and used future could find alternatives and transformation (Inayatullah, 2008) through restoration and inclusion of care in human relations. The discussion draws upon interviews and focus groups held with school teachers in Rio de Janeiro, in relation to a broader research on documentation practices. Following feminist theorist Karen Barad (2007) and post-colonial studies (Spivak, 2010), we exercised diffraction as a research methodology, not separating reality representation from reality construction, yet attentive to mapping past, present and future through "not taken-for-granted" assumptions, about "future-making". Such a view of education recognizes the dynamic emergence of agential matter in classrooms, curriculum and policies, and makes us aware of the creative and inseparable "other" (Taylor, 2017). In our study, despite precarious resources and lack of public support, teachers proactively showed sensitivity and care. Students were challenged to be active participants on building better imaginaries. These practices inspired learning processes, and give voice and agency to the socially excluded, allowing for alternative thinking to the obviousness of colonial and oppressive relations and decisions.

Exploring the sociotechnical imaginaries of aid to research *Veronica Brodén Gyberg, Linköping University*

The promotion of science and technology for development has been a part of public aid actors' agendas and interventions since the 1960's, with the purpose of counteracting the unequal distribution of resources for research in the world in different ways. Some actors have explicit ambitions of escaping a colonialist heritage by underlining the importance of local ownership and local priorities, but there is debate concerning whether the goals and methods of aid actors have the intended effects or whether research aid risks contributing to a scientific neocolonialism of sorts. The theories of change underlying these interventions vary depending on donor actor and country context, but traces of different development theories and theories of science can be identified in the trails of these science for development discourses. In this paper, I build on my previous study of the Swedish pioneer research aid actor Sida-Sarec and present some preliminary findings on recent discursive

development, exploring how the links between science and technology and development have been portrayed during this past decade. The work is based on text analysis and interviews and uses the concepts of sociotechnical imaginaries and boundary organization in order to explore why and how states support science (Jasanoff & Kim, 2009; Guston, 2001). This issue is placed at the intersection between science and development politics, areas that sometimes have conflicting goals. The case of research aid illustrates this tension well, and I can therefore hopefully contribute the development-related, postcolonial and decolonial discussions within STS.

Shaping Expectations of Hybrid, Partial and Conflicted Conjugated Subjects for Living with Technoscience in a Post-COVID World *William Leeming, OCAD University*

At the end of the pandemic, we are often told that we can expect to live with an assortment of “new normals” in the future. Furthermore, we are warned not to fixate on returning to “old normals.” We are instead told to pay attention to and remember what was foretold prior to the pandemic concerning the imminent rise of natural and human-made disasters in the future. At the same time, it has been suggested that human societies in a post-COVID world will be better equipped to face a series of longstanding challenges which include tackling anthropogenic environmental harms and a range of inequalitarian social arrangements in need of rectification. This paper focuses on identifying key stumbling blocks to thinking about tackling anthropogenic environmental harms combined with rectifying inequalitarian social arrangements in shaping expectations of new normals. It shows what today has led to a perceived need to reinforce the resilience of neoliberal subjects to preserve productivist and consumptionist ways of living. Alternatively, this paper makes a case for a conjugated subject to question and replace the totalizing efficacy of neoliberal programs of resilience. Warwick Anderson originally coined the term “conjugated subject” over a decade ago to express the surfeit of meaning and significance attached to technoscience in postcolonial STS contexts. This paper proposes a conjugated subject who refuses programs of resilience at the expense of even-handed relational and communal needs, and who promotes the use of technoscience for solving the rifts between humans and the world and one another.

Session Organizer:

Martin Andrés Perez Comisso, SFIS - Arizona State University

335. Academic Automation: Machine (un)learning /Artificial (non)intelligence - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Over the last 70 years, computational and networked media have become deeply integrated with higher education and have slowly adopted and integrated various technologies. The newest generation of technologies engaging higher education centers around what is popularly called artificial intelligence, otherwise known as machine learning. Machine learning creates models that, in part self-design solutions that may include interaction, prediction, and other simulatable aspects. This paper argues that significant elements of human interaction and democratic education are demonstrably lost when elements of the educational milieu are automated. While there are plenty of automatic grading examples, artificial teaching assistants and robotic instructors already occurring in specific contexts, and those are seemingly claimed successfully in those contexts. Also, one has to admit that if we are to treat people as humans, we cannot give humans jobs that could be performed entirely by an automaton because otherwise, we would just be treating the humans as if they were automatons. That said, this paper uses examples from the new crop of AI/Machine learning companies and the related discourse to argue that what they teach, communicatively, isn't necessarily what should be taught if we are to have a democratic society. The discourse tends to ignore democratic issues in favor of matters of labor and efficiency. However, in the research, teaching, and service environments of higher education, while labour issues

are prevalent, they pale to governance problems, human communicational literacies, and strategic wisdom core to democratic learning. Following Ivan Illich's unlearning, this paper uses that evidence and argument to show that as human educational technology progresses, it envelops the ideas of the institutions it exists within. I argue that this will parallel the unlearning and unintelligent AI systems as they have to 'learn' and be 'taught' from increasingly less capably educated populations, creating a spiral to the bottom. Thus the parallel interaction between decreased human interaction from a weakened democratic education combined with the increase in machine-assisted learning will undermine the machines' capacity to learn, which will then feedback into the system, weakening it further. This can be resisted both by choosing better technologies and changing the discourse to center on the priorities of higher education, which should be the creating a free society with educated citizens who can communicate effectively in pursuit of the good life (or some variation thereof). With that sort of direction, the ai/learning machines can be trained specifically to those or similar human goods.

Participants:

“Automating Ourselves Out of Our Jobs?”: The Automation of Science in a Science Automation Lab *Vlad Schüler-Costa, University of Manchester*

This paper draws from my ethnographic engagement within a “science automation lab”, in which scientists developed AI and robotics solutions to automate microbiological experiments. Here I discuss the effects these scientists considered their research might have in the practice of science itself, particularly when faced with the question of whether they were building systems which would, possibly, replace their labour and put themselves out of employment. Drawing from their statements and from critical university studies, I show how they consider these concerns to be unfounded and misleading: rather than worry about robots replacing scientists in the future, they worry about not getting stable employment in the current academic system.

On following the rules: Auto-testing in Computer Science Education *Samantha Breslin, University of Copenhagen*

Part of programming often includes automated checking and testing for errors: by the compiler, by unit tests made by the programmer, and by auto-testing systems for assignments, to name a few. Drawing on auto-ethnographic reflections on studying computer science in Canada, as well as ethnographic research on undergraduate computer science education in Singapore, this paper explores the long-standing practice of auto-testing in computer science education. Such testing practices have been common much before current trends in ‘auto-grading’ based on machine learning and artificial intelligence. Indeed, tests by compilers and interpreters are built into the practice of learning to program; at the very least, students must learn to write code that functions, which requires that it passes the compiler's tests. For assignments, students also ideally write code that functions properly, and so passes tests by their own test programs or the auto-testing systems designed for assignments. The compiler and auto-tester then become the arbiters of correctness of student assignments. This paper considers how passing such tests requires that students learn to follow computational rules down to details such as the placement of semi-colons in code or the number of spaces in output. In doing so, students learn to operate within computing “worlds.” The paper suggests that such practices may have contributed to normalizing auto-assessment and prediction technologies in computing, feeding into current computational trends.

Online classes as solutionism: Can a LMS be convivial? *Edward Maclin, University of Memphis*

The last two decades have seen an increase in the number of online university classes operating under any of several commercial Learning Management Systems (LMS). Online classes expanded dramatically in the US during 2020 as a response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Students, faculty, and administrators frequently assume that LMSs are

epistemologically and ontologically neutral. These LMSs are designed to do exactly what they say on the tin: they are systems for managing learning. At the same time, they function based on implicit understandings of “learning,” “management,” and “systems” that privilege some knowledges, interactions, and discourses while de-emphasizing others. Specifically, these systems tend toward a focus on knowledge-as-thing over knowledge-as-process. In this paper I argue that the LMS as a tool is not—in the terms of Ivan Illich—convivial. Rather, LMSs as designed enforce a technocratic perspective based on efficiency and replicability. At the same time, problems with LMS-hosted classes are defined in technological terms, with additional improved software being seen as the main solution. I argue that carefully considering the LMS as a medium for coursework can allow instructors (and students) to draw on the platform’s strengths without submitting to the logic of the LMS as a tool.

The Prof in the Machine: Ghost Labour, Presence, and the (De)Automation of Online Learning *Nathan Rambukkana, Wilfrid Laurier University*

During the Covid 19 pandemic, educational institutions across age categories have leaned on automated, online, and remote learning in unprecedented ways. A best practice held up in training for remote instructors is developing a feeling of “presence,” of proximity and intimacy between (and among) students and instructors so that those taught feel a sense of connection to those teaching and each other, and by extension greater engagement with the course and material. But what happens when part or all of the teaching of courses is automated? When courses lean heavily on machine learning tools and machine organized structures, the instruction exists on a continuum from cyborgian extension (in which, in the best case scenario, AI and algorithmic tools can “informat” (Canzonetta, 2021) lower level pedagogical tasks to leave more time and energy for more intensive instruction (one-on-one writing feedback, for example), to ghost labour (Gray & Suri 2019) in which Amazon Mechanical Turk-like piece-work, or contract human labour services, are used as back-ends for seemingly automated even autonomous AI teaching systems. When the prof is part of a broader machinic assemblage of diversely situated actors and actants, when and how is the elusive goal of “presence” at risk? From the shock and disconnect of discovering your remote class’s canned lectures are from a deceased prof, to the unexpected depth of connection that forms of online engagement can foster, this paper maps the territory of machine-assisted teaching in search of what enriches the pedagogical experience, and what decimates it.

Of Ofqual and A-Levels: Understanding the Effects of Algorithmic Bias on Students *Sanaa Khan, UC San Diego*
Predictive analytics and algorithms have shown to include racial bias in many different contexts, including education (Noble, 2012; Barocas and Selbst, 2016). Discrimination resulting from such systems in education only compounds existing issues of student equity. Most recently, this has come to a head in the 2020 Ofqual grading algorithm for A-level exams that left students in U.K. state schools, often with a higher number of BAME students, scored lower than students in private schools. The Ofqual algorithm was touted as a way to neutrally assign A-level scores in the light of pandemic precautions interrupting usual testing; instead it made students in lower-income and racialized communities vulnerable, putting student futures at risk. The consequences for this biased algorithmic intervention are still being felt by the U.K.’s minoritized student population. This paper explores the effects of Ofqual’s sorting and grading algorithm on BAME students in the United Kingdom. What is the lived experience of Ofqual A-level algorithmic sorting for minoritized students? What meaning do minoritized students ascribe to the use of Ofqual A-level grading and sorting algorithms in their schooling? Student narratives were gathered and analyzed as case

studies that demonstrate the fragility of the idea of a “neutral” algorithm. I aim to present a living historical account that highlights the precarity of algorithmic intervention in educational spaces; considers how social paradigms are encoded within algorithms; and centers the voices of marginalized, racialized students in the sphere of educational technology.

Session Organizer:

Jeremy Hunsinger, Wilfrid Laurier University

336. Can it scale? Big Tech, entrepreneurship, the scalability zeitgeist, and the role of STS - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Participants:

Can it scale Coming to terms with the new scalability zeitgeist in innovation and public policy *Sebastian Michael Pfothenhauer, Technical University Munich; Brice Laurent, ARMINES; Kyriaki Papageorgiou, ESADE Business & Law School; Jack Stilgoe, University College London*

An obsession with “scaling up” has captured current innovation discourses and, with it, economic and political life. Perhaps most visible in the rise of platform technologies, big data, and concerns about a new era of monopolies, scalability thinking has also permeated public policy in the search for solutions to “grand societal challenges,” calls for “entrepreneurial statehood”, or scalable transformations through “living labs.” In this paper, we explore this scalability zeitgeist as a key ordering logic of current initiatives in innovation and public policy. Building on STS literature that has primarily focused on non-scalability and its ensuing frictions, we are interested in how this explicit preoccupation with scalability reconfigures political and economic power by invading problem diagnoses as well as normative understandings of how society functions and who authorizes social change. By looking at three sites – platform technologies, living labs, experimental development economics – we identify three constitutive elements of how scalability thinking is being rationalized and operationalized across these diverse settings: tech solutionism, experimentalism, and future-oriented valuation practices. Our analysis offers a new vocabulary for understanding and critiquing current modes of innovation that increasingly value scaling as an end in itself, and opens up spaces for proposing alternative trajectories of social transformation. It further suggests that STS’s engaged program needs to come to terms with the “politics of scaling” as a powerful corollary of the “politics of technology.” If critical analysis wants to perturb dominant discourses on the relationship between innovation and social change where it matters most, then our theoretical frameworks and modes of intervention must go beyond the insight that universalism is impossible.

From “Scaling Up” to “Deep Scaling”: the Politics of Experimental Innovation in French Hydrogen Mobility *Alexandre Violle; Brice Laurent, ARMINES*

Numerous innovation projects have been launched in recent years to develop hydrogen mobility. Many of them are framed as “experiments” that would be first steps before cars, production and charging stations are scaled up, possibly at national or even bigger levels. Building on empirical materials collected in 2020 and 2021 about hydrogen mobility development programs in France, we investigate various experimental projects and their replications. We seek to problematize the obsession with “scaling up” that is visible in the hydrogen sector as in other technological domains. We identify a tension between a discourse of rapid scaling for nation-wide deployment, and projects undertaken by local authorities and private companies who make small-scale experiments with hydrogen cars and charging stations more and more dense, by adding uses, actors, and technical functionalities. We use the terms “deep scaling” to characterize the latter approach. By examining the technical, economic and social

components of deep scaling, we discuss its geographical and regulatory consequences. In this configuration, technologies are not expected to expand to vast territories by remaining the same at a bigger scale. Instead, they are attached to local sites and develop alongside them, which raises the issue of the connections between those sites. The analysis of deep scaling allows us to identify potential alternatives to ready-made discourses of scalability, and contribute to the STS analysis of the politics of scaling.

It's Not The Market, Stupid: On The Importance of Non-market Exchange in Scaling Innovations for Sustainability Transitions *Dominic Glover, Institute of Development Studies; Koen Beumer, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University; Harro Maat, Wageningen University*

The obsession with 'scalability' is highly visible in the field of sustainability transitions. Driven by a sense of urgency about planetary catastrophe, both sustainability theories and practices are strongly shaped by the requirement for their interventions to be scalable. In this paper, we examine and dissect the main mechanism for scaling in theories of sustainability transitions: the market. Defined as exchanges mediated by money where prices are established through supply and demand, sustainability theories widely assume that market formation is critical for sustainability innovations to scale. Their recommendations therefore focus largely on promoting commodification and market exchange. We criticize the assumption that markets are central to scaling on two accounts. First, empirically, we use the case of the System of Rice Intensification (SRI) to demonstrate that sustainable innovations can travel widely without relying on market exchange. Drawing on earlier studies and fieldwork in India (Prasad, Beumer & Mohanty 2007; Maat, Venot & Glover 2017), we show that this innovative method of rice cultivation traveled to farmers across India through non-commercial exchanges (and its travels would be obstructed when creating the markets that are envisioned by sustainability theories). Second, theoretically, we criticize the reconfiguration of political and economic power that comes with the reliance on markets. Drawing on work in economic history and anthropology (e.g. Polanyi 1944; Mauss 1950; Graeber 2011), we argue that understanding scaling as being 'embedded' in a wider set of institutions for exchange, is empirically more accurate and opens up the politics of scaling to democratic considerations.

Scalability Thinking in Health and Ageing Innovation: A Critical Analysis of its Working and Effects *Carla Greubel, Utrecht University*

In a critical response to the design of much STS research on technology as single case studies focusing on processes of domestication/appropriation/localization, STS scholars Hyysalo, Pollock and Williams propose 'biographies of artefacts and practices (BOAP)' as analytical framework and methodological tool to analyse how technological innovations are not only localized but also generified. Generification work refers to strategies used in the design and implementation of technologies that allow these innovations to travel across contexts by embodying characteristics that are common across users and use contexts. In this paper, I bring the STS discussion on generification versus localization together to critically explore the idea of 'scaling' that has become a prominent notion in many European innovation discourses and technology implementation projects. In particular, I investigate scalability thinking through a study of discursive and material practices of generification and localization in the H2020 large scale pilot project on smarter living environments, GATEKEEPER (2019-2023). In this project, 8 pilot regions spread across seven European countries employ a range of digital health and care innovations with the aim to scale up 'best practices' to other regions in Europe and beyond. Drawing on an analysis of project documents,

participant observation during meetings, and interviews with partners from each of the pilot regions and consortium members, I discuss the working and effects of scalability discourses and practices as a matter of both localization and generification work. For STS, this sheds further light on the tension between - but also the interweaving of - these two contrasting concepts.

Session Organizer:

Sebastian Michael Pfotenhauer, Technical University Munich

337. Networking Rurality Part 1

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Rural communities' information infrastructures are slow to build out and prone to breakdown, potentially hampering their economic opportunities. Technology companies are addressing these challenges by developing new networking capacities for farms and rural communities, often with state-based support and incentives. Rural connectivity is promised to transform the provision of data to, and collection of data from, rural and remote areas, and thereby to transform rural life. But will such transformation be positive and seamless? What approaches might STS scholars bring to bear to critically analyze the digitalization of rural life? For instance, what pre-existing mechanisms of social cohesion in farm and fishing communities might be disrupted by the push to digitalize? Will networking technologies which enable economic mobility also place pressures on rural practices to conform to urban imaginations? Will rural information connectivity projects follow state-supported infrastructure projects like rail, telegraph and telephone, which led to the consolidation of agricultural and communications industries? How does high-bandwidth information communication access and its effects vary based on geopolitical contexts and relative wealth of rural communities? This panel seeks to explore the intersection of the rural (and ideas of the rural) with novel ICT technologies like internet infrastructure provision. It examines how the possibilities and problematics of networked rurality are co-constructed by technology developers, rural residents, and policy makers, and how they are shaped by or diverge from long histories of rural expropriation. The panel will also speculate on how emergent technologies could be channeled into alternative trajectories.

Participants:

Data-driven Trust in Rural Cultures of Hunting *Norman Makoto Su*

Data-driven technologies promise new, effective ways for institutions to establish trust with stakeholders. We describe how a US Department of Natural Resources agency in a Midwest state has mobilized data-driven technologies in order to establish trust with deer hunters. Hunting is intertwined with the state's efforts to protect and preserve wildlife and their habitat - fees and licenses account for the majority of the DNR's operating budget. Yet, hunting is in a crisis, with a 30% drop in licenses since 2006. The DNR has implemented data-driven initiatives involving citizen science and online, real-time access to collected data to allow hunters to both participate in and understand data-driven decisions. These efforts attempt to mend a previously distrustful relationship between government agencies and the rural public. Drawing from interviews, we describe the "folk models" hunters hold in understanding how data is being used to inform DNR scientists and policy makers. We find that hunters have developed a localized perspective of data, extrapolating it to global trends. While appreciating open access data from the DNR, hunters spoke of the rhetorical role of data instruments - how instruments demonstrate the worthiness of hunters' values and opinions. Lastly, while the "folk" in "folk models" may imply a misunderstanding or lack of rational thought, we argue that these models are actually quite logical. It is crucial to understand and use, not dismiss, folk models if we desire data-driven technologies to serve a bridging and translating function that grounds productive conversation with rural communities.

Data Crematoria: An SF Island Where Data and Its Energy Are Renewed *Laura Watts, University of Edinburgh*

Data Crematoria is a mythical island. This is where data is sent to die. Like many speculative islands it is a remote place, hard to reach, but home to those who live and farm there. This is where the energy required to make data—to make one separable from zero—where that energy is renewed. Farming data and energy from the land and sea is already everyday life for many rural communities. It is often in the cold far reaches where you find sea-cooled server farms and renewable energy wind farms side-by-side, feeding the internet habits of the world. On mythic Data Crematoria the locals have worked hard to create their own self-determined data and energy future, to farm their island as they have always done, and to provide a unique service back to the world. This speculative fabulation (an SF as per Donna Haraway) draws on my recent ethnographic collaboration with the virtual power plant project, ReFLEX, which has established a local energy company on the northern islands of Orkney, Scotland, to flexibly balance renewable energy generation and demand across grid, heating, and transport infrastructures using data. Inspired by additional work on data heritage this SF explores data and energy farming in a rural community for the far future.

Overcoming Place Through Space: Constructing Rural Identity Through Satellite Internet Infrastructure *Donny Persaud, Cornell University*

Satellite internet has emerged as an economically viable alternative to resolve long standing infrastructural deficits hindering rural internet access. Silicon Valley based companies such as SpaceX promise affordable broadband internet through Starlink, their network of low-earth orbit satellite constellations capable of bypassing existing material constraints on connectivity. However, the launch of Starlink satellites has generated significant controversies regarding their qualitative effects on night skies in rural places and their effects on astronomical knowledge production. Infrastructures are a material expression of their developers values implying certain practices and ways of living at the expense of others. As private technology firms and governments seek to connect rural communities, these communities point to the detrimental effects brought by infrastructures that interfere with rural practices and values. This talk explores these controversies around the development of new internet infrastructure and how these embody different understandings of what rural places can and should be.

Un-common Relations and Rural Community Networks *Nicola Bidwell, International University of Management Namibia*

Shared use of small-scale natural commons, such as forests, fishing grounds, pastures, water and wildlife, are vital to the livelihoods of over two billion people, particularly rural inhabitants. Rural women have been most committed to defending the commons since privatization restricts their independent access to resources for every day subsistence and their involvement in a meshwork of cooperative relations. The failure of market-based approaches to provide rural connectivity in low to middle income countries (LMICs) also acutely affects rural women, who have much less access to telecommunications than rural men or urban women. Thus, potentially, rural women would gain most from Community Networks (CNs), or locally owned, managed and operated telecommunications networks, that treat the internet and telephony as a public good and are oriented by the commons. Yet, my studies suggest rural CNs in LMICs do not tend to value the relations that women form when they produce, reproduce and use the commons. I draw on multi-sited ethnography of international advocacy for CNs; interviews and observations of CNs in rural India, Indonesia, Argentina, Mexico, Uganda and South Africa; and participation in a CN in rural Namibia. My analysis suggests that un-common relations are produced when male biases in CN technoculture and advocacy and rural governance combine with the commodification and selective valorisation of labour in the prevalent paradigm of innovation.

Ground Truth: Datafication of Regenerative Futures *Matthew Kearnes, Environmental Humanities Programme, School of Humanities and Languages, University of New South Wales*

Earth processes are increasingly being enrolled as unwitting, and at times reluctant, accomplices in efforts to address anthropogenic environmental change. Part of a broader project focused on 'terrestrialising carbon', soil carbon sequestration and regenerative agriculture practices have emerged as technologies of eco-social optimism. Marshalled as a response to a raft of contemporary sociopolitical and environmental problems, the retention and long-term sequestration of soil carbon and the promise of regenerative agriculture encode soil and farming with political atmospherics that are simultaneously speculative and hopeful. At the same time, technologies of precision agriculture, 'climate smart farming' and remote earth observation are increasingly enrolled in accounting for subterranean carbon concentrations and projects of regenerative landscape management. Focusing on landscape regeneration projects in the British uplands I explore the digital work engaged in accounting for carbon in restored peatlands. Situated in the twin shadows of the political devolution of the United Kingdom and the withdrawal of the UK from the European Union, I argue that the interface between landscape restoration and the technologies of digital visualisation are characterised by forms of epistemological bricolage in the context of long-term struggles concerning rural land use in the British Uplands. I conclude by suggesting that while the curation of new data infrastructures for remote earth observation and carbon mapping is heralded as providing the conditions for new forms of knowledge, practice and evidence – such infrastructures are also enrolled in the navigation of altogether more terrestrial political geographies.

Session Organizers:

Jen Liu, Cornell University

Phoebe Sengers, Cornell University

Kelly Bronson, Department Of Sociology And Anthropology, University Of Ottawa

Matt Comi, University of Kansas

Discussant:

Phoebe Sengers, Cornell University

338. Commodified Relationships: the politics of intimacy and resistance

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Participants:

Anti-MLM: A Consideration of Creative Labor, Identity, and Multi-Level Marketing Resistance on Social Media *Megan Sawey, Cornell University, Department of Communication*

Recently, and especially during the COVID-19 pandemic, perhaps one of the most notorious remote labor opportunities is multi-level marketing (MLM). MLM companies produce a variety of products, ranging from kitchenware to essential oils. Independent distributors purchase these products and sell them to people within their personal networks, often through social media. They may also earn money by persuading their peers to become distributors. According to the Direct Selling Association, multi-level marketing is a multi-billion-dollar industry. Arguments against MLMs unfold on the same platforms that enable their proliferation. Indeed, after decades of lost wages and relationships, people are wrestling control of platform affordances to build a network of pushback against an industry rooted in gendered labor divisions, consumerism, and the commercialization of social life. This project utilizes semi-structured interviews with anti-MLM YouTube channel owners. These creators have carved out a popular niche on the platform, to which they contribute lengthy livestreams and commentaries on problematic MLM participants and practices. At the same

time, their voices resonate on Reddit, Instagram, and other platforms -- where users participate in parasocial-type discussion of the creators' videos. I explore creators' motivations for their MLM resistance and consider how creators evaluate the credibility of anti-MLM content. In light of the money creators might earn from YouTube, Patreon subscribers, merchandise, and other sources, they must situate themselves amidst the seeming contradictions of anti-MLM advocacy and their commercialized content. Thus, I argue that channel owners blur the socio-technical boundaries of digital resistance and the digital culture industries.

Distal Intimacy: the ASMR community and the transformation of care *Patricia Ciccone*

Two decades ago, members of a Yahoo community calling itself Society of Sensationalists started to share links of seemingly unrelated content. The content they shared ranged from how-to videos to promotional clips from beauty parlors. Although disparate in subject matter, all shared items had been tagged by the members of the community for their ability to trigger pleasurable physical reactions among those who considered themselves sensitive to a phenomenon now known as Autonomous Sensory Meridian Response (ASMR). While these exchanges started in the early days of the Web, the Society of Sensationalists has now grown into a significant, large-scale online social community. Moving away from found footage that was collected and circulated in the early days of the community, video producers with global visibility now tailor their content directly to receptive fans that follow their videos with passion. This paper examines the roles that algorithms and platform policies play in shaping how this content gets created, interpreted, shared and archived. By paying close attention to the shift from the impersonal link-sharing of extant and found videos to the personalized, confessional register of the videos that are produced today specifically for a target audience, I investigate how "acceptable" intimacy is defined and performed in the context of digital commercial platforms and what the limits imposed on such work entail for the political potential of care. I argue that caught between the intimate private sphere they so often emulate (via whispering and direct narrative engagement) and the context of publicness they are constrained to use for their distribution, namely YouTube, ASMR videos become the perfect object to highlight the contradictions of intimacy as it relates to the neoliberal discourses of affective labour and care.

Epistemic Empathy as Methodology *Yvonne Melisande Eadon, UCLA*

This paper explores ways to cultivate epistemic empathy as part of methodological practice. Epistemic empathy, which can be considered an integral part of feminist methodology, serves as a method for developing different kinds of researcher reflexivity, and can also serve as a method for cultivating productive and healthy relationships with other researchers, interviewees, journalists, and members of the public. Social applications of epistemic empathy, such as using it as a way to converse with individuals who are in the thrall of QAnon or similar phenomena, will also be briefly explored.

Intimacy-as-a-Service: Entanglements of Invisible and Emotional Labor in Digital Sex Work *Ellen Kaufman, Indiana University Bloomington*

Commercialization is often positioned as anathema to intimacy; the prevailing normative view of emotions and economics asserts that money "morally contaminates" intimate experiences and vice versa. In the context of service work, however, emotional interests regularly intersect with financial considerations, requiring careful negotiation of the boundaries between work and home, business and pleasure, and private and public spheres. In her seminal research on emotional labor, sociologist Arlie Hochschild outlines how distinct affective commodities are produced within the postindustrial service-based marketplace. In

today's "gig economy," nowhere is this more apparent than within the mainstream sex industry, where the growing prevalence of personalized, digital platform-based sex technologies reflects an emerging paradigm of sexual labor centered on the exchange of authentic emotional and physical connection. In this paper, I illuminate how these platforms orchestrate the boundaries of intimate sexual commerce by providing a multifaceted infrastructure through which clients' diverse and specific emotional needs can be met. By rendering mostly invisible the transactional nature of these interactions and amplifying the authenticity of these services, these technologies alleviate some of the underlying tensions associated with the purchase of intimate care. From the workers' perspective, however, these affordances significantly increase the amount of invisible labor required of performers, often simultaneously replicating and exacerbating many of the existing race- and class-based power asymmetries within the industry. Exploring the contours and complex assemblages of the platform-based sex industry offers unique insight into the challenges and implications of commodified relationships from both an economic and interpersonal STS perspective.

Nutrition Claims in Multi-Level Marketing and the Spread of Dietary Confusion *Carlin Soos, University of California, Los Angeles*

Multi-level marketing companies (MLMs) frequently offer questionable research and dubious claims in support of their dietary supplements and "wellness" products. When mixed with the intimate anecdotes, beliefs, and economic goals of individual sellers, incorrect information regarding the efficacy of a product—and nutrition in general—can quickly spread throughout a person's social network. Yet the politics surrounding MLM sales are undoubtedly complex: while there are real consequences to both this business model and its proliferation of false nutrition claims, the products may be alluring to those who have struggled to address their diet or health concerns through more conventional means. This paper will discuss particular motivations for purchasing MLM food products and supplements, the regulations surrounding their labeling in the United States, the external influences that have fueled their demand, and the complicated relationship between buyer and marketer.

Waitresses invisible labor in the United States: An invisibilization due to the many assimilations between waitresses and traditional female figures. *Lucie Mezuret, Université de Paris*

My communication will start by stating a paradox: waitresses' bodies are omnipresent in the lives of Americans and yet invisible. I will assert that this invisibilization is due to the many traditional female figures waitresses are associated with. Waitressing is a female profession (over 70% of the employees are women). Therefore, waitressing is mostly unrecognized because it is associated with domestic labor. However, I will argue that waitresses are asked to emphasize this association. They are required to perform the part of the wife, the mother, the mistress, the servant. They must shape their bodies and their attitude to meet the expectations of the customers. They are asked to talk, to walk a certain way. There is a theatricalization of their bodies. The uniform that they must put on exemplifies that idea. Here the notion of aesthetic labor will be analyzed. The main reason is to get better tips which represents the main part of their salary. Indeed, nowadays in America, in many states, the sub-minimum wage is \$2.13 per hour [Bureau of Labor Statistics]. Hence, they must rely on their social encounters with customers to make a decent living.

Session Organizer:
Yvonne Melisande Eadon, UCLA

339. Transforming the Development & Governance of

Pharmaceuticals - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Major changes are underway within the pharmaceutical sector that are associated with shifts in research, innovation and business models from blockbuster products intended for large patient populations to more niche products designed for smaller, more targeted populations. Innovation is underway in how drugs are being researched and developed, and how they are being manufactured, used, evaluated, licensed and paid for. While some of these changes are tied to genomics and the rise of personalized medicine, others result of patient activism and disease politics. These technical and political developments put pressure on public regulators and payers, resulting in novel forms of governance, including the use of real world data and conditional reimbursement. This panel builds on STS scholarship on the socio-technical production of pharmaceutical knowledge, as well as its material and biopolitical impacts. We invite papers from a range of international perspectives that critically analyze these transformations, as well as those that highlight forms of alternative pharmaceutical practices and methods that are more sustainable and offer more just and equitable access to treatments. Topics may include but are not limited to: – Forms of open pharmaceutical innovation – Industry dynamics and changing business models – Patient groups and new forms of knowledge production – R&D partnerships across public, not-for-profit and/or private sector – Drug repurposing and off-label use – Changing regulatory knowledge and forms of evaluation – Pharmaceutical pricing and access – Novel access arrangement and alternative regulatory frameworks for coverage – Future health care system sustainability and social solidarity.

Participants:

Mapping a controversy: Identifying issue publics through discourse and social network analyses of #rarediseaseday.

Matthew S Hanchard, University of Sheffield

Healthcare costs have risen dramatically in the US and Europe over the past three decades, especially for rare diseases (Makami, 2017). Government incentives have sought to entice pharmaceutical companies into developing and producing low profitability medicines, such as those used to treat rare diseases (Gronde, Uyl-de Groot, and Pieters, 2017). However, there has been a market shift around these incentives towards orphanisation based business models (Vogler, Paris, and Panteli, 2018). Here, defined diseases are separated into genome-specific subtypes, with drugs marketed to patients within each subtype as a quick and efficient form of personalised medicine (Trible and Lupkin, 2017). This has fostered disproportionately high costs for many rare disease treatments (Makami, 2017). In response, patient organisation (PO) networks like EURORDIS and NORD have voiced patients' and patient groups' concerns by advocating for better access and lower costs while seeking meaningful solutions, such as working collaboratively with clinical researchers on repurposing existing drugs (Davies et al., 2017; Hernandez et al., 2018). In turn, their work has garnered a great deal of public engagement and interest in healthcare interventions for rare diseases, providing opportunity for patients and patient groups to contribute in new ways towards the shape of drug policy and legislation. This paper draws on discourse and social network analyses of online discussion of 'rare disease day' to identify a set of issue publics that coalesce around particular narratives and counter-narratives. In doing so, the paper provides valuable insights into the way knowledge is formed around rare diseases and orphan drugs.

Time to 'SPIN' out: Novel R&D partnership for patient access to high-cost drugs for rare diseases. *Vanessa I Scanga, Osgoode Hall Law School, York University; Conor Douglas, York University*

"You get what you pay for" rings ever true for people living with a rare disease where the trade-off for high-priced treatment is an improved quality of life or a bona fide life saver. Treatment for rare disease is not one option among many; it is often the only option among the few. The price of pharmaceuticals in Canada

are among the highest in the world. But for rare disease, the price is typically higher still and evidence of their effectiveness limited by the capacity to amass threshold data under the gold standard of random control studies. These challenges are not unique to Canada, but they are symptomatic of broader networked challenges unique to Canada's biopharma landscape. While bilateral government agencies are key supporters of public-private partnerships in R&D spending for neglected diseases in Canada, there is little evidence of these partnerships for rare disease drugs. Socially innovative approaches, such as "social pharmaceutical innovation" (SPIN), offer alternate ways for stakeholder partners to work together and correct limitations of the traditional linear biopharma innovation model. One promising approach is to better coordinate support for research from the range of stakeholder scientific and economic data. Our look at Toronto's M4K Pharma program and its open science platform aims to reimagine R&D partnerships under a SPIN approach. The broader implication of moving beyond the high price tags and uncertain data that characterize current options for rare disease treatment serves as a blueprint prescription for the equitable delivery of health care for all Canadians.

Pharmaceuticals as Matters of Collective Concern *Mette B. Steffensen, Danish Ministry of Industry, Business and Financial Affairs; Christina L. Matzen, AbbVie; Sarah Wadmann, The Danish Center for Social Science Research*

Public and patient involvement (PPI) is promoted as a means to ensure the legitimacy of decisions to promote or restrict access to new medical technologies. Building on Habermasian ideals of deliberative democracy, current policy solutions aim to engage patients as experts of lived disease experience and promote consensus among healthcare managers, clinicians, patients and manufacturers on the value of new pharmaceuticals. Focusing on health technology assessment (HTA) practices in the Danish healthcare system, we explore how patients' engagement in the evaluation of specialized therapies corresponds to these ideals of PPI. The analysis rests on document analysis and interviews with four employees of the Danish HTA agency and 14 patient representatives. We identify a schism between regulatory conceptualizations of patients' 'experiential expertise' and medical 'evidence' and demonstrate how the ideal of consensus sometimes prevent rather than facilitate deliberation. Drawing on and contributing to STS scholarship on the epistemic identity of patient organizations, we show how patients' responses to these challenges vary considerably: while some dismiss their acclaimed role as patient 'experts', others seek to adapt their 'experiential expertise' to scientific ideals or invest in 'evidence-based activism'. We discuss implications for the ability of patients to turn medical technologies into matters of collective concern.

Supporting Reflexivity in Medicines Development: Opportunities and Challenges to Developing a Tool for Monitoring and Evaluating Patient Engagement Initiatives *Callum Gunn; Tjerk Jan Schuitmaker-Warnaar, Athena Institute; Lidewij Vat, Athena Institute*

Medicines development is faced with enduring pressures, coming to be associated with various accounts of stifled innovation models, resulting from reward structures promoting the development of expensive medicines and/or those offering little therapeutic benefit to patients. Meanwhile, recent years have seen a proliferation in the number and diversity of activities, organised by established development and governance actors, that directly involve medicines users and carers in innovation practices. Patient engagement (PE) thus may present new arrangements of practice that attempt to deal with these recurring problems. Drawing on the system innovation literature, we framed the IMI-PARADIGM project ('Patients Active in Research and Dialogues for an Improved Generation of Medicines') as an emergent form of systemic innovation practice, taking place deep within an

incumbent sociotechnical regime, that can be supported by intervening activities that promote reflexive modes of practice. In co-leading a work package of the PARADIGM project, which focused on constructing a tool for monitoring and evaluation of PE initiatives (24 PE cases in total, organised by the pharmaceutical industry, patient organisations, and regulatory/HTA bodies), our project activities aimed to promote reflexivity for supporting PE initiatives. After outlining our intended double function of the tool as a device for standardization of reflexivity, this paper will explore the opportunities and challenges faced by this strategy in facilitating reflexive modes of practice in the medicines development context. Our findings seek to contribute to debates on embedding of reflexive monitoring as part of system innovations, and interventionist STS more broadly.

Session Organizers:

Conor Douglas, York University

Paul Martin, Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield

Tineke Kleinhout-Vliek, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University

Chair:

Tineke Kleinhout-Vliek, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University

340. STS as Whiteness? Towards Decentering Whiteness in STS - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

In 2018, Michael Mascarenhas described STS as a white space through how its programs, institutions, leadership, and inquiries perpetuate white supremacy. This often emerges as colorblindness, an ideology of unmarked whiteness where anti-racism is assumed to accomplish anti-racism. Although existing STSers work to decenter United States and European geographies and genealogies as the sole sites for STS, many sites of whiteness in STS remain black boxed. Given the position of STS to shape and intervene in technoscientific knowledge production and policy, it is urgent for STSers to actively deconstruct the whiteness that is reproduced in our work. In thinking with the conference theme of Good Relations and the urgency of making and doing STS in ways that decenter white supremacy, presenters will explore what it means for STS and STSers to decenter white supremacy. This includes discussions about the reproduction of whiteness in STS and the alternative relationalities required to decenter whiteness in our scholarship and practice. Over the course of two sessions, presentations will address questions, including, but not limited to: How does STS (including tacit notions of who/what is STS) reproduce whiteness? How might pressures to institutionalize STS or form disciplinary identities foreground whiteness? How could discussions about the whiteness of STS mask existing critical race, postcolonial, decolonial, and ethnic studies scholarship in STS? What possibilities are there for decentering whiteness in conceptual frameworks, pedagogies, scholarship, programs, and practices of STS? How might we strategize such that non-white scholars are not disproportionately burdened to decenter whiteness?

Participants:

Race, Racism & Bioethics: A Structured Review *Natasha Richmond*, University of Toronto

The field of Bioethics has deemed select subjects as deserving of inquiry, funding, research, and time: conversations about bedside ethics, lifeboat ethics, and new biomedical technologies predominate, with a focus on issues such as organ transplantation, genetic engineering, triage, and medical assistance in dying. In contrast, topics related to racism, social determinants of health, or health disparities are considered outside of the scope of the field, or unworthy of bioethical attention. This review outlines how mainstream Bioethics has historically interacted with, understood, and omitted the question of race and racism, and summarizes criticisms of and recommendations for the discipline. The literature identifies

whiteness as the primary epistemological structure that shapes bioethical membership and scholarship, thereby influencing the conceptual frameworks and values foregrounded in the field. White, Western Christianity has also been viewed as instrumental to the field's development. Central criticisms include its reliance on notions of objectivity, egalitarianism, colourblindness, and post-racialism that fail to account for the reality of racism and other oppressive systems. Passivity, the shirking of accountability, over-preoccupation with the Tuskegee Syphilis Experiment, and historical and racial amnesia are also discussed. Recommendations for future directions in the field include the development of a "Black Bioethics" that focuses on Black health and experiences, and incorporates Black philosophical and activist traditions. Bioethics must also develop a broader and richer practical repertoire that extends beyond the confines of academia; move beyond exclusively medical paradigms; and incorporate diverse analytical strategies, such as Critical Race Theory and post-colonial theory, into its intellectual practice.

From postcolonial approaches to postcolonial practices in STS.

Francesca Battista, Virginia Tech STS

Science and Technology Studies had adopted a reflexive criticism leading to a more inclusive approach in terms of voices and frameworks. Recently, for example, Asian concepts have challenged Western ideas that still characterize academic exchanges between Western and non-Western settings (Law and Lin, 2017). However, conferences related to postcolonial studies, calls for papers shaping the academic agenda, and printed books we write and read, mainly take place in, and come from institutions that work synergistically to preserve the Western cultural hegemony. The mentioned practices expand the Western countries' cultural capital and convert it into economic capital. This conversion takes place, for the individual, through professional advancement and increase of salary, and at the collective level, through the sale of Western products (conference revenues and literature, among others). This paper suggests that changes in topics and methods should match STS practices. Through the lenses of Bourdieu's sociology, the implicit homology between the political field and the intellectual field of STS becomes clear (Hess, 2013). Postcolonial STS community practices might end up in turning inclusivity into cultural appropriation and exploitation. Although an academic community cannot change the global order, it can choose practices aiming at cultural capital redistribution. I propose to revise ideas of translation, publishing, and financing to better integrate non-Western countries. These suggestions could be implemented quite easily by scholars, especially seniors who already have a big cultural capital to invest. Otherwise, interesting exotic books are added to our shelves, as coffee and chocolate were added to the European diet.

Demechanizing Whiteness: Lessons from Theatre of the Oppressed *elizaBeth Simpson*, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

Group participants carry with them the social habits and norms of their culture, which are in turn informed by a dominant culture that shapes social norms and expectations. (Poole, Seibold, and McPhee, 1985) Thus, all groups, including knowledge-making groups, will inherently carry and replicate social the dominant culture. This means that, in a culture undergirded by white supremacy, researchers, informants, and administrators alike will carry into their practices the tenets of white supremacy, and any decision-making practice will allow for the replication of power imbalances unless they are specifically counteracted. That is to say: if a practice is merely "neutral" towards the social climate of the group the process will replicate bias and oppression simply by creating a space in which participants play out their inherited patterns unfettered. Therefore, any group wishing to avoid replication of oppression will need to actively employ anti-oppressive practices. Demechanization, a technique developed by participants in the Theatre of the Oppressed, is one such practice.

The Theatre of the Oppressed (TO) provides small group techniques to strategize and “rehearse” for collaborative liberation using popular education forms of systems analysis, bolstered by practices that counter implicit biases and habituated behaviors. This paper draws on interviews with “jokers” at Centro de Teatro do Oprimido in Brazil to advocate the need for continual engagement of demechanizing techniques in knowledge-making practices, including STS, in order to demechanize the tenets of white supremacy culture and undermine its prevalence.

STS and/as Anti-Racism *Martin Abbott, Cornell University; Ellen Abrams, Cornell University; Amanda Almeida Domingues, Cornell University; Shoan Yin Cheung, Cornell University; Cat M Coyle, Cornell University, Department of S&TS; Faridah Laffan, Cornell University; Hannah LeBlanc, Stanford University; Lissette Lorenz, Cornell University; Jason D Ludwig, Cornell University; Meredith A. Palmer, Department of Science & Technology Studies/ Cornell University*

In reaction to racial disparities during the Covid-19 pandemic, the increasing infiltration of white supremacist ideas into mainstream American political discourse, and the historic protests against racism that arose in the wake of the police killing of George Floyd, a group of graduate students, postdoctoral researchers, and alumni of the Department of Science and Technology Studies (STS) at Cornell University have come together to formulate strategies for making and doing anti-racist STS research and pedagogical praxis. We have started building a reading list, running a reading group on STS and racism, and initiating regular conversations with department leadership about issues of inclusion, diversity, and equity in our department and the university as a whole. Despite our many accomplishments, there is much still to be done to create a space where all voices can be heard. In this paper and conference presentation, we share our experiences, strategies, and challenges with the intention of starting conversations about how university departments can foster STS and/as Anti-racism. Two important questions that we will discuss are: how do we recognize activist and interdisciplinary anti-racist work in an academic system that rewards mainstream and traditional contributions? How do we acknowledge the past and continued whiteness of STS and especially its canon while also centering anti-racist work, including work not always recognized as “STS”?

Session Organizer:

Gabriel Medina-Kim, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

341. Data / Care: Relations, Affects, Practices - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

As digital data continues to rapidly proliferate, sustained by the ever-expanding architecture of the cloud, discussion of “data management” has become ubiquitous. Individuals, institutions, and states are all faced with the onerous work of organizing, culling, and keeping track of their data, raising questions that range from the stakes of self-archiving to the environmental costs of large-scale data storage (Hogan 2013). This panel proposes a new approach to these now-common problems, asking: does it make sense to talk about data care? When we center the people tasked with “managing” data in our analysis, questions of relationality inevitably arise. Is something like care at work when a data center technician sustains terabytes of data through his everyday practice, or saves it in the face of natural disaster? What kind of relating is at play in a researcher’s process of ensuring her data set is “clean”? What do intense affects associated with “data hoarding” and data loss tell us about normative expectations of care (Dow Schüll 2017)? By positing care as a flexible center point in this conversation, we aim to dig deeper into the relationships between people and the data they are responsible for. Topics of discussion may include, but are not limited to: - Design and maintenance of digital infrastructure - Questions of data privacy, ownership, and sovereignty - Non-human and

new materialist approaches to data relations - Gendered histories and practices of data care Session I of this two-part panel is organized around “Data for Caring”; Session II is on “Caring for Data.”

Participants:

Care and Communities Behind House Data? A Home Monitoring Experience in the Chilean Patagonia *Gloria Baigorrotegui, Instituto de Estudios Avanzados - Usach; Karla Vidal, Institute of Advances Studies; Gabriel Reyes, Institute of Advances Studies*

The installation of monitors in a remote city in the Chilean Patagonia is exceptional and aims to evaluate public policy in an innovative way, accessing data regarding the environmental behavior of homes in real time, through an open access platform denominated the Red Nacional de Monitoreo (ReNaM) (National Monitoring Grid). However, in March 2021 only two of the ten monitored houses registered data and over time the gaps are frequent. Due to this missing data, the paper refers to digital state experiments, relying on infrastructure, care and reparations studies. Specifically, it considers the question of the possibility of identifying communities and, from there, recognizing which communities and care are brought to the forefront and which are left out of sight. Thanks to a digital ethnography, the analysis of everyday practices and discourses of those in charge of public policy concludes that the rhetoric used by the authorities to eradicate undesirable behavior, by way of intervening in the name of scientific data and comparable experiments, puts their legitimacy at risk by neglecting predominant heating systems based on firewood and self-building, as well as the maintenance of material infrastructure (hardware) of the data. Given this situation, we recommend distinguishing between access and connection in data infrastructure, and drawing from this, questioning the delay in improving the health of its inhabitants occasioned by the neglect of ecological monitoring.

Caring For The Patients or Caring For Their Data? Ethnography of an Online Psychotherapy Platform *Shai Satran, Hebrew University of Jerusalem*

Israel’s public health service is actively introducing an online psychotherapy platform. On the website’s landing page, above the username and password fields for login, and just below the ministry of health logo, the following message appears: “Throughout this site avoid using any identifiable personal information, like surname, physical address, email address etc.” This is not a trivial guideline for a therapeutic interaction which includes text-based communication with a therapist: a space where the patient is meant to feel safe enough to share any and all personal, often extremely private, information. Why does this warning appear then? The short answer is that the servers of this cloud-based therapy platform are located in Sweden, well outside of Israel’s borders. Following three years of fieldwork (participant observation) accompanying this computerized intervention’s journey from lab to public integration, I will describe how the adherence to data localization guidelines prompted a series of tradeoffs between data concerns and clinical sensibilities; while both are framed as caring for patients, it is a process that crystallizes what is deemed worthy of protection and what is not. The digital therapeutic is too often thought of solely through the aspect of human-computer interaction. However, the data ensuing from the interaction, and the accompanying care that data requires, constitute an important factor that loops back into the core of the therapeutic process. How do we define what is personal and private, and what is worthy of care, once we take the role of data into consideration?

Cutting the Feeling: Affect and Digital Memory in “Storm Data and Unusual Weather Phenomena” *Jeffrey Moro, University of Maryland*

From 1959 to the present day, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) of the United States has

published "Storm Data and Unusual Weather Phenomena," a monthly report comprising all severe and otherwise extraordinary weather events throughout the country. Issues of "Storm Data" blend quantitative information on storms' tracks, severity, and damage to life and property with qualitative accounts of the weather events themselves. These accounts, which range in length from single sentences to tens of thousands of characters, draw from a range of sources, including the National Weather Service's own forecasts, eyewitness testimony, law enforcement, and local media reports. With nearly two million recorded weather events and hundreds of thousands of unique narratives, "Storm Data" provides an opportunity not only to understand the quantitative aspects of severe weather, but also how such events enter into an official meteorological-historical record. Following the work of scholars such as Sara Grossman and Paul Edwards, this paper analyzes "Storm Data"'s publication history and data stewardship practices, particularly since its shift from paper to digital records in 1993, to argue for renewed attention to the roles that affect and judgment play in the production and maintenance of climate data. Through both close reading individual narratives and engaging large-scale macro-analysis using techniques drawn from the digital humanities, this paper demonstrates how "Storm Data" produces a sense of historical authority through the flattening of affect, even as individual traces of subjectivity still erupt in its pages and data files.

Data Care During Crisis: A Comparative analysis of COVID data infrastructure builders in India and the USA *Ryan Ellis, Northeastern University; Janaki Srinivasan, International Institute of Information Technology - Bangalore; Megan Finn, University of Washington; Bidisha Chaudhuri, International Institute of Information Technology Bangalore; Stacey Wedlake, University of Washington; Amelia Acker, The University of Texas at Austin*

Who does the work of making and circulating data about a crisis? How does the social location of these workers shape practices of "data care"? We explore these questions in the context of producing COVID dashboards, contributing to the software that underpins COVID data infrastructures, and maintaining tools which enable other forms of data processing or visualizing COVID data. COVID data infrastructure builders undertake this work in different contexts all over the world. This paper will present an ongoing collaboration between researchers in India and the USA exploring the production of local and national COVID-19 data infrastructures in these countries. Critical COVID data infrastructures are continually being designed, maintained and managed by varied actors such as, government agencies, academic research institutions, news organizations and philanthropies, and grassroots community organizations run by volunteers, activists, archivists, and librarians. Different geographies and institutional ecologies (resource constraints, trust in data or institutions, data collection practices and policies) shape these projects. Within a project too, the work done by these data builders can look different based upon their role. A project will involve a range of data work from designing data flows; identifying a data source; collecting and cleaning data; deciding how/what of it to present. Far from being neutral platforms, these systems present particular visions of the pandemic; they offer stylized representations that both illuminate and conceal. Using different COVID dashboard projects, we examine the categories and hierarchies of data care to understand how these layers of context -- regional, social, political, role-based -- shape the hierarchies of data care.

Care in Conflict: Working with Smart Technology as Discursive and Material *Madison Snider, University of Washington*

Resisting the simplification of care as inherently beneficent, feminist STS scholarship challenges us to think with care as non-innocent, including care for data. This paper argues that the

practices of care in built environments networked with smart technologies illuminate care orientations in conflict some of which involve care for data but also extend to care for space, community, and energy resources. This paper draws on ethnographic research on the role of care practices necessitated by various stakeholders in a smart university campus. Increasingly networked within the Internet of Things (IoT), the shared built environment of a university campus is ripe for data extraction. The rise of smart devices requires labor with things, articulated with hands and bodies, as well as speculation and ideation, articulated with minds and mouths. The complex phenomena of work with smart technologies can be understood through an analysis of the ways a diverse set of stakeholders talk and act to maintain, repair, and care for infrastructures that are material, informational, and social. Through an analysis of discursive and material care practices as constitutive of interdependencies of infrastructures, this paper evidences care in conflict. Smart devices, championed for their potential for discovery, innovation, and sustainability, are simultaneously understood as cybersecurity, privacy, and operational risks. Care, as a practice, is constitutive of knowledge creation, organization, and policy. This paper provides evidence that care for smart technology as speculative and ideal is not always conversant with care for smart technology as embodied and actual.

Caring data and information systems: towards a digital permaculture *Nathalie Grandjean, University of Namur, Belgium*

It is widely agreed to think that we have entered a "digital age". There are, however, a number of scholars who are convinced that we have entered the Anthropocene, an era of instability which is threatening our way of life, ecosystems and hence the survival of the human species. It is therefore legitimate to question the possibility that our world remains digital if it suffers from extreme ecological devastation? How to think about the future of the Web and the digital at the time of the Anthropocene? Our proposal is speculative and is inspired by the ethical principles of permaculture (Holmgren, 2014). Permaculture, both ethical and practical, is guided by three major principles: "(1) take care of the Earth and all its forms of life, (2) take care of people (...) and (3) redistribute the surpluses (to the Earth and to people)". In addition, permaculture is not dogmatic, because it is the detailed observation of the "environment" and its interactions that will determine the particular design, necessary for resilience. It is therefore not a question of applying principles to soil, but of taking care of both the processes and the living people inhabiting this space. As Puig de la Bellacasa maintains, "permaculture is an ethics of care, but also an a-subjective relational ethics, addressing humans and non-humans with the idea of taking care of living environments together, including humans and more-than-humans" (2017, 161). We find inspiration in this ethical and practical model of permaculture in order to re-think the way digital objects and cultures should be designed and implemented.

Session Organizers:

Alix Johnson, University of Florida
Steven Gonzalez, MIT

342. Evidence-based Medicine? Regulating Vaccines, Drugs and Other Health Products during COVID 19 and Beyond-I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Facing an untamed pandemic, governments have leveraged public trust and perhaps health in facilitating good relations with industry in co-producing innovative health products in record time. Established evidence-based medicine standards have been overshadowed by the deployment of new regulatory mechanisms such as Emergency Use Authorizations (in the US and UK), Interim Orders (Canada), and Conditional Marketing Authorizations (European Union) that have expedited Covid19 diagnostics, therapeutics, and vaccines to an anxious public, despite partial and uncertain clinical trial "results." To unpack this trend, which capitalized

upon pre-pandemic social alliances and regulatory modernization agendas that emphasize agility, flexibility and innovation, and its impact upon the future of health product regulatory practices, papers in this session will address one or more of the following lines of inquiry: • Investigating the shifts in regulatory approaches, practices, and responses that confirm or counter the perceived erosion in evidence-based appraisal of health products; • Offering theoretical, empirical and especially ethnographic findings that characterize the political economy or structural drivers of the changes in health product governance before and/or during the pandemic, and their implications for post-pandemic futures; • Attending to new modes of biopharmaceutical knowledge production, including alternative therapies, such as psychedelic-assisted therapies, that disrupt entrenched relations between regulators and ‘big pharma’ in the wake of Covid19 and evolving standards of safety and effectiveness. Engaging with critical analyses of how knowledge and evidence is shaped by powerful vested interests, such as the pharmaceutical industry, the session will contribute to STS scholarship on the governance of evidence.

Participants:

Buying vital goods: The case of PPE markets during times of crises *Nurgül Özbek, Stockholm School of Economics, Institute for Research (SIR); Linus Johansson Krafve*

This paper addresses the making of collective concerns in markets for Personal Protective Equipment (PPEs) during COVID-19. While such ‘concerned’ PPE markets are expected to solve a public issue by providing a vital good, they operate under an economic logic where the performativity of economic transactions allocates resources and shape collective concerns. The paper presents a pilot study of buying practices in PPE markets in Sweden, the EU, and the UN. We ask how these buying practices shape the market sensibilities of PPE markets? Our analysis highlights how such sensibilities amplify or demote collective concerns in specific ways. This includes the devotion in PPE markets to local or global societies, matters of fairness, accountability and equitable distribution. Our findings tap into contemporary discussions about the performativity of markets in times of crisis, as we contribute with conceptual knowledge needed to construct more civilized markets for PPEs. These findings also open up a space to investigate the role of STS scholars in in shaping collective concerns in markets for vital goods.

Reproducing Exclusion: (Evidence-Based?) Vaccination Practices and the COVID-19 Trials *Anna Wynfield, University of Colorado Boulder*

In December 2020, the FDA authorized two vaccines for COVID-19, relying on data from a standardized population of human research subjects. Yet while these data demonstrated safety and efficacy, there were certain categories of people—including pregnant individuals—who were excluded from participating in the trials. Such exclusions are not atypical. Considered a vulnerable population, pregnant people have historically been restricted from taking part in many clinical research trials. Nevertheless, with only limited data about the effects of the COVID-19 vaccines in pregnancy, dominant organizations including the Center for Disease Control and American College of Obstetricians and Gynecologists have issued guidance suggesting that the vaccines should not be withheld from people who are pregnant. Noting the increased risk of severe COVID-19 illness during pregnancy, such statements have largely emphasized that the choice to vaccinate should be a personal decision made in consultation with a healthcare provider. Although the first trial to test vaccines in pregnancy began in February 2021, vaccines had already been made available—and administered—to tens of thousands of pregnant people prior to this time, many of whom were reproductive-age healthcare workers and educators. Drawing on 40 ethnographic interviews, my paper explores how pregnant individuals have conceptualized decisions to vaccinate in the absence of evidence-based data. In deferring vaccination

decisions to personal choice, I argue, the United States has established a precedent of experimentation by default, through which individuals independently consent to embrace personal responsibility—and testing occurs outside the framework of a structured clinical trial.

Will Psychedelic-Assisted Therapies Benefit from COVID-19? Frictions, Evidence, and the Future of Regulation of Alternative Therapies *Agnieszka Doll, Dalhousie University*

The COVID-19 pandemic and the governments’ investments in developing medical countermeasures to tame the virus’s spread reiterated and facilitated ongoing pharmaceutical regulatory modernization processes in Canada. While the discourse of flexible clinical trials design and a rolling assessment of trial evidence has explicitly been linked to the COVID vaccines and therapeutics developments, such discursive and regulatory changes are likely to have broader system implications for the assessment of alternative therapies, which do not squarely fit into the biomedical framework for evidence production. This presentation draws on ethnographic interviews with community agents involved in developing psychedelic-therapies and regulators who, as institutional agents, impose and/or authorize certain pharmaceutical knowledge production practices. I will attend to various ‘small’ moments from these regulatory encounters to illuminate the emergence of multiple ontologies of evidence at the nexus of the COVID accelerated ‘modernization’ and psychedelics regulation in Canada.

Session Organizer:

Agnieszka Doll, Dalhousie University

Chair:

Matthew Herder, Director, Health Law Institute, Associate Professor, Faculties of Medicine and Law, Dalhousie Univer

Discussant:

Janice Graham, Dalhousie University

343. Conspiracy Theorists and Techno-Science - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

Techno-science, and the changes wrought by techno-science, frequently result in pushback. While such resistance can be grounded in attention to risks and social justice issues, this resistance can also take the form of conspiratorial reactions. From climate change denial to anti-vaccine movements, from fears of 5G towers to UFOs, from pseudoscience to conspiracy theories—instead of settling contentious debates, the creation of techno-scientific evidence has repeatedly led to conflict over what it is that particular evidence truly shows. Not simply consisting of a rejection of techno-science, conspiracy adherents marshal government documents and scientific reports in order to push for conclusions other than those found in those materials; with many conspiracy advocates learning to skillfully deploy the language of expertise in order to bolster, and spread, their claims. This session engages with the conference theme of “good relations” by approaching the matter of relations from the opposite direction. We seek to investigate the sorts of “bad,” “inappropriate,” “conspiratorial,” or “unforeseen” relations that emerge from modes of techno-scientific expertise and knowledge making. In what ways does the same evidence get mobilized by groups with differing agendas to advance bizarre claims? How have different media technologies afforded the efficient spread of such thinking? Beyond treating them as a source purely for concern or derision, what can (or should) STS scholars learn from studying pseudoscience and conspiracy theories? Beyond an assemblage of case studies, we hope our panel will demonstrate how views that are often treated as unserious deserve serious critical attention.

Participants:

Bye Bye, Blue Skies of Trust in Science Gabriel Dorthé, IASS Potsdam / Harvard STS

In times of mounting worries about fake news, conspiracy theories, vaccine hesitancy, or other measures against the Covid-19 pandemic, prominent actors call for restoring trust in science

(among them the President of the United States or the WHO). Drawing on an ongoing ethnographic research (online observation and semi-structured interviews), I suggest that the relationships between science(-based) policy and citizens need more entanglements, instead of an irenic restoration of public trust by means of education or debunking initiatives. The upsurge of conspiracy theories regarding sociotechnical issues such as solar geoengineering or 5G deployment can teach us key ingredients about the reception of technoscientific promises and the distribution of legitimate expertise in the public. Do people involved in some degree of belief and spread of conspiracy theories distrust science, or do they trust it too much, up to, for instance, raising concerns towards the injection of nanobots that have been promised in grand narratives since the early 2000s, or up to demanding an immediate stop to stratospheric chemical spraying, as some prominent scientists present this scheme as a potential efficient measure to counteract global warming? How do they marshal relevant facts and make sense of them? What counts as trustworthy, for whom, at which cost? How is trust and suspicion negotiated among these groups, and potentially stabilized? What do these pressing issues tell about the shifting relationships between the local and the global, my body and the planet, my freedom and the common good, or the naked-eye perception and the invisible?

Hype or Conspiracy? Narrative Convergences in Techno-Hype and Conspiracy Theories *Stephen Hughes, Science and Technology Studies, University College London*

“A neuralnanorobotically enabled human brain/cloud interface might serve as a personalized conduit [...] to engage in fully immersive experiential/sensory experiences, including what is referred to here as ‘transparent shadowing’. Through transparent shadowing, individuals might experience episodic segments of the lives of others”. This quote doesn’t come from an obscure blog about the Great Reset, but rather from a 2019 paper from *Frontiers in Neuroscience*. In this panel, I would like to discuss the convergences between hype and conspiracy imaginaries, and what the implications are for the political relationships between science and society. I will draw on research I am conducting as a responsible innovation consultant on a European research project that is developing touchless haptic technology using neurocognitive AI. I will discuss the narratives that researchers use to imagine the technology and its applications (e.g., the movie *Demolition Man*) and how these narratives converge with conspiracy imaginaries of bio-applied AI as a plot to enslave humanity. I will suggest that this convergence reveals how technoscientific hype narratives are drawn upon in conspiracy theories and amplified through a politics of mistrust, alienation, cynicism and fear. Despite how bizarre conspiracy theories might appear, they are plausible and meaningful to many people and guide their interpretation of technoscience and the motivations behind it. I will conclude by suggesting that this raises important questions about whether or not, or to what extent, we might consider conspiracy responses as forms of public engagement and how we might address that given their typically dangerous politics.

Look at the Numbers!: Interrogating Conspiracy Networks and Scientific Communication Online *Melina Sherman, New York University*

Nearly every day, we are confronted with headlines that warn of the rising death toll, of new infectious variants, and the possibility of new vaccines for combatting their spread. We are flooded with information about the crisis – much of which is based on rumor, disinformation, and misinformation. This paper combines theories and methods from communication studies with those from STS and public health to understand how social media communities on Facebook, YouTube, and Reddit are being used by conspiracy adherents (specifically, networks of anti-masks and anti-vaxxers) to communicate scientific information in ways that bolster and spread their claims. In doing

so, it seeks to offer new understandings of the ways in which crisis communication online is formed and the ways in which conspiracy theorists’ scientific communication practices organize the broader social landscape of the pandemic. Examining the ways in which science and crisis communication evolve in online conspiracy networks is crucial for understanding how public data is and can be leveraged - whether to build resilience among communities faced with a crisis or to spread disinformation that threatens the wellbeing of those same communities. Using knowledge gleaned from in-depth online fieldwork and interviews, this project seeks to contribute to the production of knowledge in STS and public policy about how we – as scientists, practitioners, and citizens – may deepen our understanding of the “bad relations” emerging from online conspiracy communities and how we might interrogate them to intervene upon today’s most troubling health problem.

The Symmetric Asymmetry. Grammars of Expertise in Evaluating Knowledge *Stefan Nicolae, University of Trier*

The literature on pseudoscience and conspiracy theories proliferated as much as the phenomenon itself. Regardless of their theoretical claims and depth, the study of alternative or pseudo-knowledge, as, e.g., pseudoscience and conspiracy theories, generally raises two analytically problems: they both test social actors’ (as well as researchers’) normative orientations towards „truth“ or „reality“ and irritate the genuine social-constructionist vein which should initially enable the research. While the first problem is largely addressed in the media and communication studies (Zimmermann & Kohring 2018, 2020), the second problem directly points at one of the cornerstone of STS: the problem of ‚symmetry‘ (and ‚impartiality‘; see Lynch 2017). Equally skeptical towards negative diagnoses of a contemporary ‚death of expertise‘ (Nichols 2017) or even a ‚death of truth‘ (Kakutani 2018) as well as towards a filiation between STS and ‚post-truth politics‘ (Collins, Evans, & Weinel 2017) my presentation generally focuses on the ways in which expertise is publicly enacted and justified. By methodologically bracketing questions on the truth claims of pseudoscience and conspiracy theories and instead looking at their claims of expertise I argue in particular for a study of ‚grammars of expertise‘ as modes of evaluating knowledge. Drawing on the empirical example of the German movement ‚Querdenker 711‘ (a melting pot of esotericism, anti-vax, alternative medical and conspiracy theories established in the dawn of the COVID-19 pandemic) the presentation takes up the ongoing discussion of ‚symmetry‘ in STS and seeks to contribute to emergent field of Sociology of Valuation and Evaluation.

Session Organizers:

Zachary M Loeb, History & Sociology of Science, University of Pennsylvania

Kate Dorsch, The University of Pennsylvania

344. Agrifood Futures in-the-Making: Part II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

With a booming agritech sector, venture capitalists, philanthropists, scientists and engineers are playing an increasingly central role in shaping agrifood futures, both through the deployment of socio-technical imaginaries and the transformation of material realities. As a result, agrifood scholars are engaging with novel technologies including synthetic biology, tissue engineering, digitization, robotics, artificial intelligence and related fields. Scholarship at the intersection of STS and agrifood studies allows for critical examination of the tensions between agritech’s aspirations to radically transform farming and food systems, and the profound ecological and social consequences these transformations might entail. Papers in these four panels offer critical insights into contested agrifood futures in-the-making. Panels I and II will explore what it means to engineer both the ‘perfect farm’ and the ‘perfect food.’ Panels III and IV will discuss contested ideologies and ontologies of food, agriculture and technology. These panels highlight the work of scholars affiliated with the

STS Food & Agriculture Network (STSFAN), a small but growing intellectual community. We also invite anyone interested in our work to join our conference Meetup to learn more about the network.

Participants:

Automation in the food factory: Processing Foods in India
Barkha Satish Kagliwal, Cornell University, Department of S&TS

Automation as it relates to agri-food is broadly concerned with its consequences for both workers and managerial control. This literature, both from history of technology & the sociological present, generally turns to changes in relations on the farm (Fitzgerald 2003). An early exception is Giedion's (1948) approach that brings to the fore the difficulty of standardizing processes in meat packing and breadmaking. Moreover, attention toward automation has mainly focused on industrial processes in the Global North and/or other industries such as paper and auto parts manufacturing (among others). In this paper I bring a Global South perspective on automation and production of food away from the farm and into the Indian food processing industry. I analyze how food production was gradually turned away from completely labor-based production to the ideal imaginary of 'food produced with no human touch' that is yet to be achieved. In addition to document analysis, I draw on semi-structured interviews with food producers to show that by co-opting food from the threshold of small-scale production, technologists & engineers face 'challenges' for: i) standardizing taste; ii) the automation of bodily gestures; and iii) capturing tacit knowledge from verbal recipes. I argue that exploring these instances where food refuses to be standardized shows an aspect of automation that has consequences for not only workers & managers; but also for analyzing food processing markets & for the food system at large.

Aesthetic Regimes in Agri-Food: The Cultural Role of Science and Technology in Modern Food Politics
Katharine Legun, Wageningen University

In this paper, I elaborate on the concept of aesthetic regimes applied to contemporary agri-food politics. This concept was developed by Jacques Ranciere (2013) in his reflections on historical shifts in the symbolic lexicon being circulated in art to recognize the social politics implicated in those shifts. For example, Ranciere describes how the 18th century frenzy over the Belvedere Torso—a headless, limbless sculpture of a human—can be seen as a revolt against the limited politics that were availed to art when its purpose was viewed as simply capturing and circulating beauty and expression. No limbs and no face in the Torso meant no expression and no beauty could be evaluated, and its celebration ushered in a new aesthetic understanding and through it, new political capacities in art. The concept, adapted, can help to clarify the relational power represented by new food aesthetics—the smells, appearances, and tastes that are made distinct and those that are made invisible. Aesthetic regimes applied to food allow for the recognition of non-humans in the ways that aesthetics is enabled and constrained by the ecological aspects of food production, but also the clarification of power relations, as the symbolic representation of food circumscribes the political roles and capacities of different actors in its cultural reproduction. In this paper, I'll discuss structural parallels in the roles of labs, breeding programs, and glasshouses in the advancement of a modern aesthetic regime exercised across synthetic meat, hops, and tomatoes. I'll use the concept of aesthetic regimes to deepen an analysis of food politics of late capitalism, and particularly the role of science and technology in these shifting symbolic landscapes.

Alternative Protein's Imagined Publics
Charlotte Biltekoff, UC Davis

In the interest of saving the world despite apparent consumer resistance to changing food habits, innovators and entrepreneurs

are increasingly promising food futures that are sustainable, ethical, healthy, delicious, affordable and familiar. In this food future consumers will apparently get to have their burgers and eat them too, especially when it comes to protein. New technologies will provide cellular cultured meat and dairy that is actually meat and dairy (just produced in a lab), mycelium steaks, plant-based burgers that "bleed" and are even more delicious than the real thing, insect flours, protein produced from "air" and other delights that will utterly transform the food system while leaving the experience of eating familiar, safe and traditional. In the wake of ongoing public skepticism about genetic engineering and other food and agricultural technologies, however, those advancing tech driven answers to the "grand challenges of food and agriculture" – centrally, feeding 9 billion by 2050 – also contend with their own fears of consumer resistance to the disruptive innovations that they have already deemed essential. Drawing on data collected on food tech companies that are based in or have come through Silicon Valley, this paper explores the politics, possibilities, and limits of how Food Tech imagines its public, especially in terms of its relationship to science and scientific expertise. Centrally, it is concerned with projections of the public's agency and capacities, how the public is imagined vis a vis scientific governance, and what this means for emerging visions of the future of food.

Session Organizer:

Karly Burch, University of Otago

Discussant:

Xaq Frohlich, Auburn University

345. Load-Bearing Bodies: Unjust Relations and Liberatory Horizons – I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This is the first session in a panel that centers decolonial, feminist science studies to explore material bodies as infrastructures that alternately stabilize and contest structural inequity. It does so by foregrounding the construction of load-bearing bodies—human and otherwise—suspended amidst the tension of unequal relations. These sessions will investigate the blurred boundaries of bodies and the structures they entail, especially those of racial capitalism and cisheteropatriarchy. Material burdens settle into bodies, embedding privilege and subjection within capacities and orientations that can be difficult to dislodge. At the same time, attuning to bodily matters can bring alternative possibilities into alignment. In this first session, we will explore plastic Barbie flesh as a hackable medium for grappling with gendered bodily norms. Digital sex algorithms reveal normative logics—white, cis-male, and abelist—of individuated consent as they are programmed into interactions between human and computational beings. Orthodox Jewish women encounter shifting hormonal bodies as they subvert masculinized dynasties in religious education. UK activists maneuver around biosexual imaginaries that tether HIV care to white, homonormative citizenship practices. Forensic identification of deceased bodies in the Mediterranean demonstrates how European infrastructures only legitimize the movement of migrating people after death. By thinking across these papers, spread through multiple sessions, we will explore how bodies become scalar archives for uneven intra-actions among technological, scientific, and ecological processes. We will address how bodily burdens maintain disparate conditions, and how bodily stuff can animate good relations for liberatory horizons.

Participants:

Activism, HIV Prevention and Biosexual Citizenship:

Embodying Marginalisation and Disruption in UK PrEP
Activism *Ingrid Young, University of Edinburgh; Charlotte Jones, University of Exeter*

PrEP (pre-exposure prophylaxis) as an HIV biotechnology has been widely heralded as revolutionary. After much battle and significant community activism in the UK, PrEP is now freely available through NHS services, but its 'uptake' has been highest amongst white cisgender gay men. How are certain bodies

imagined as 'beneficiaries' of PrEP and how does this shape biotechnological activist imaginaries? In *Sex, Drugs and Activism* we explored UK PrEP activism, and were particularly interested in how identities, communities, and practices were entangled with the biosocial of HIV prevention, producing what Epstein (2018) terms biosexual citizenship. Where we explored how notions of (cis) gay men's bodies and sexualities shaped the orientation and achievements of activism (Jones, Young, Boydell 2020; Young 2021), we also asked how the bodies of those often at the 'margins' of access were affected by dominant PrEP activist imaginaries. Through observation in activist spaces and in-depth interviews with activists who identified as/worked with trans and non-binary communities, sex workers, people who inject drugs, and people of colour, we explore how biosexual imaginaries shaped citizenship practices in the context of biomedicalized HIV prevention. This presentation considers how activists navigate cis/homo-normative, white structures to secure access to and/or make sense of sexual health technologies, and how activists position PrEP within their own health imaginaries and priorities for resistance to ill-health and harms. Ultimately, we ask if and how PrEP might preserve structural inequity, or as a 'revolutionary' HIV biotechnology, might distract and disrupt ongoing struggles, creating new opportunities for social change.

Yeshiva Bodies: Explorations in Hormonal Ethnography *Shira Schwartz*

My paper takes us from male rabbinic yeshivas in the ancient Middle East to contemporary American Orthodox female yeshivas in Jerusalem, and to bodies whose sex/gendered processes change during immersive Torah study. Since late-antiquity, yeshivas have operated as sites of Jewish male educational reproduction. "Yeshiva" signifies both the scholastic bodily position of sitting and an institution. The male body has long been the site of this learning and its reproductive processes, bringing male rabbis and disciples into proximity for face-to-face educational transmission. Yeshivas sex bodies rabbinically, with reproductive processes and sex/gendered features that are specific to the yeshiva's ethnoreligious transmission. The exclusion of women and female bodies from yeshivas, and their elision within Jewish rabbinic textual practices, has enabled yeshivas to operate as spaces of male reproduction, desire and authority. Indeed, women's bodies are likened in rabbinic texts to houses, while their reproductive domestic labor upholds the yeshiva's foundation. But what happens when the foundation moves and reveals itself as body; when the location of learning changes to a different kind of sex/gendered body? I introduce hormonal ethnography as a method to trace how bodies change as they move in and out of institutions that for thousands of years have created Jewish men. How might we engage the study of sex/hormones as an ethnographic practice that connects bodies with their locations of production, and how might doing so enable us to understand the dynamic capacities of bodies lodged in supportive roles against themselves?

Technological Bodies, Animating Access, and Consenting Fictions *Josef Nguyen, The University of Texas at Dallas*

This paper examines technologies constructed as artificial bodies in order to investigate the force of "consenting fictions" in recognizing autonomous subjecthood. For instance, Roxxy Gold's robotic sex doll Frigid Farrah is programmed to perform refusal of consent, while Robert Yang's sex game *Hurt Me Plenty* renders the player's ability to play dependent on the digital game character's trust in them. Both examples demonstrate how, beyond representing fictional consenting agents, technologies can simulate consenting subjects capable of sexual play that express distinct understandings of consent. With Frigid Farrah, the pleasure sold derives from violating the doll's bodily consent through a rape fantasy. For *Hurt Me Plenty*, the game's granting of access to the digital character's body through the framing of trust mandates consent before play. By exploring how we animate nonhuman technologies to simulate consenting

agents as one form of consenting fiction, this paper interrogates the fictions about consent that grant human autonomy under Western possessive individualism. This paper draws together science and technology studies, media studies, as well as feminist and queer scholarship on consent to investigate technologies presented as artificial consenting bodies as a supplemental space for exploring consenting fictions as technologies in themselves for animating human subjecthood, particularly to differentiate subjects and their bodies. Ultimately, this paper examines what is at stake when we animate technological access through consenting fictions in a social world constituted by normative white, cis male, and ableist logics that prescribe how human bodies are to acquire the juridical recognition of consenting subjecthood altogether.

Moving Bodies. Drowning and Creative Infrastructures of Identification *Sara Casartelli, Sapienza, University of Rome -- Department of Communication and Social Research (CORIS)*

This article empirically analyses how the unknown bodies of migrants who died in the attempt to reach Europe are managed and potentially identified. Shifting attention away from the border, the paper provides a new angle to the crisis unfolding in the Mediterranean, investigating the practices developed in order to know and attend to the dead migrant's body. More specifically, drawing from 6 months of ethnographic fieldwork conducted in Sicily in 2016 and 2017, the article presents an ethnographic account of the emergent Italian forensic infrastructure. It does so by looking at movement. The movement of bodies towards identification. The pursuit is informed by Science and Technology Studies (STS); the focus is on the socio-material practices aimed at the eventual identification of unknown bodies. Taking stock from recent debates in the anthropology of infrastructure in which scholars critique the idea that infrastructures are passive architectures comprising circulations, I propose an alternative perspective on infrastructure, arguing that infrastructures are processes of constant and creative adjustment and that these ongoing changes are the effect of circulation. The argument is developed in two steps. First, looking at the movement and circulation of bodies and bodily material in the infrastructure whose purpose is identification I show that the forensic infrastructure is enacted through this very movement. Second, foregrounding the material and social practices to identify an unknown body, the paper argues that circulations are performative events, that change things and people as they move through space and time.

The hackeret Barbie. First results from a participatory workshop about social pressure of body performances. *Federica Manfredi, Institute of Social Sciences; chiara pussetti, University of Lisbon*

The workshop "La Barbie hackerata" [The hackeret Barbie] has been organized for the first time at the World Anthropology Day 2021 by the team "Excel - The Pursuit of Excellence" as methodological experiment to interrogate participants about body's perceptions, its modifications and body-performances in daily life. Participants re-created their corporality on a doll in a guided-process: which body-interventions can make the Barbie, a symbol of gendered perfection, more similar to me? In other words, how do I manipulate and construct my self through my body? We discussed cosmetic surgery, tattoos, anti-aging treatments, clothing choices and diet regimes under the entanglement of social excellence and personal well-being. Aiming to stimulate an anthropological gaze on participants' bodies, the workshop revealed gendered, aged, political, cultural and hidden meanings related to body interventions, as well as fragilities and emotional negotiations with perceived social pressures on how to properly perform through the body. Recent Covid-experiences crossed childhood episodes in participants' narrations: through our works on the metaphorical plastic-flesh,

the dialogue focused on disparities for the access of body treatments, gender discriminations and the pressures we experienced as teenagers, women, workers and members of a society supposed to pursue idealistic colonial and hierarchical models of beauty, perfection and excellence. This paper is based on the project 'EXCEL - The Pursuit of Excellence. Biotechnologies, enhancement and body capital in Portugal', founded by the Fundação para a Ciência e a Tecnologia (PTDC/SOC-ANT/30572/2017) - Instituto de Ciências Sociais - Universidade de Lisboa.

Session Organizer:
Shira Schwartz

346. Innovation and Inequality in Health and Medicine - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm
4S 2021 Virtual: 21

This session investigates how experimental medicine, novel therapeutics, emerging medical technologies, and new diagnostics shape, maintain, and connect to social inequalities. The session addresses how race, gender, class, and other forms of social stratification impact access to and the development of innovative medicine. We are interested in who receives new therapeutics, to which problems or conditions medical attention and innovation attend, and the role of trials and experimentation. Papers might address questions such as: Who stands to benefit from emerging medicine? Who can access new therapies once they are commodified? How are funds and attention applied to - or withheld from - different types of disease? How does medicine drive or reproduce social inequalities? How are vulnerable people or bodies selected as test subjects for emerging therapeutics? We also invite papers that engage with the conference theme and address instances of good (or better) relations among researchers, participants, therapeutics, and illness communities. Here, we seek to consider if and how medical innovations respond to social inequalities, and if we can imagine a more equitable and just approach to experimental medicine. We welcome papers that tie STS research and theory to these concerns and are interested in a broad range of topics and approaches that address tensions between innovation and inequality.

Participants:

Equity Implications of Innovations in Care Delivery: The Case(s) of Direct-To-Consumer Telepharmacies *Ben Curran Wills*

Emboldened by an enthusiastic capital market and manifest inefficiencies, the United States healthcare marketplace is being innovated upon at high speed. Among innovations in drugs and devices, care models have also been the focus of 'disruptors' dollars. Direct-to-consumer telepharmacies constitute a young (less than 4 years old) and already multibillion dollar industry that aims to streamline the patient/consumer's health/wellness journey. Rather than the traditional model of care, where patients identify an issue, make an appointment, and see a provider about that issue a week or several later, DTC telepharmacies target potential consumers with targeted advertisements about a specific condition - perhaps most famously, phallic cacti for erectile dysfunction from leading DTC telepharmacy hims - and take the user down a streamlined purchase experience. The next thing the consumer knows, they are a virtual patient receiving an automatically renewing mail-order subscription for male pattern baldness, erectile dysfunction, or performance anxiety, just several among many available conditions that can be treated by these companies. As startups first, healthcare companies second, direct-to-consumer telepharmacies orient their business strategy around rapid growth. This orientation has profound implications for equity in care delivery. With few exceptions, these companies do not accept insurance, which means that any benefits of this care model are restricted to those that can pay out of pocket (or are lead to believe that there is no other way these generic, long-available drugs and wellness products can be accessed). Their innovations in efficiencies, such as smart patient questionnaires that ask all and only the right follow-up questions, prefer patients that are simple: cis, no risky behaviors, no comorbidities. Finally,

the conference's calls to focus on relation highlights the ways in which direct-to-consumer telepharmacies refashion the care relationship from that of the traditional provider-patient dyad (itself worthy of complication) to that of a consumer and brand. In exploring these areas, and in particular the possibilities of good medical relations under a consumer framework, this paper pulls from a multidisciplinary literature on (bio)medicalization, medical sociology, bioethics, and health STS.

Making the Shot: The Search for an Injectable Contraceptive and the Technopolitics of Birth Control, 1952-1992 *Quinn Anex-Ries, University of Southern California*

In this paper, I examine how Depo-Provera – the first commercially available long-term injectable contraceptive – was created, distributed, and used as a pharmaceutical technology for controlling and reforming non-normative sexualities. By tracking Depo-Provera from its first clinical trials at the McCormick Hospital in Thailand, to its use as a therapeutic intervention for patients at the Johns Hopkins Sexual Disorders Clinic, to its domestic clinical trials at Grady Memorial Hospital in Atlanta, this paper studies how anxieties about global overpopulation, teenage pregnancy, welfare dependency, and sex offenders were malleably applied to justify and promote the experimental use of Depo-Provera. In so doing, I explore how the production of Depo-Provera was guided by the ways that doctors, researchers, and lawmakers imagined specific patient populations as ideal drug candidates and, in turn, how political and cultural ideas about excessive reproduction and sexual deviance shaped drug development. I deploy a Feminist STS framework to examine archival and primary source materials from the Upjohn pharmaceutical company, the U.S. federal government, hospitals and mental health facilities, scientific journals, women's health activists, and newspapers. This paper ultimately reveals how racial, class, and sexual hierarchies structured the creation and dissemination of Depo-Provera, highlighting the promise and perils of experimental medicine and technological innovation.

Pregnancy, Biomedical Knowledge Production, and Inequality *Miranda Waggoner, Florida State University*

The Covid-19 pandemic has prompted many calls for the inclusion of pregnant women in vaccine trials. Although some pharmaceutical companies announced plans to begin Covid-19 vaccine trials with pregnant women in 2021, pregnant individuals were left out of the initial trials for Covid vaccines, leading to disparate and uncertain recommendations for pregnant people considering the vaccine. While the Covid-19 crisis has rendered visible the problem of gaps in evidence for medical interventions or treatments during pregnancy, Covid-19 does not present a unique circumstance when it comes to lack of safety data on vaccines or therapeutics in pregnancy. Historically, pregnant women have been left out of innovations in medicine, and clinical care for pregnant individuals currently lacks a robust evidence base due to the fact that they are routinely excluded from biomedical research studies. Drawing on textual materials from and interviews with multiple stakeholder groups, including scientists, clinicians, and patients, this paper examines the shifting landscape of biomedical knowledge production about vaccines and therapeutics for pregnant individuals. In this work, I bring together STS and bioethics literature on inclusion, vulnerability, and risk to discuss how a particular population group is positioned in relation to the benefits of emerging medicine, and I discuss how this arrangement matters for a maternal and child health arena characterized by persistently troubling rates of adverse birth outcomes and health disparities.

The Two-layered Gendered Responsibility of (In)fertility in the Context of In-Vitro Fertilization Treatment— How Fertility Specialists Practice Strategic Gendering to Manage Uncertainty *Wen-ling Kung, State University of New York at Albany*

Mainly based on interviews with 42 fertility specialists in

Taiwan, this paper shows how reproductive responsibility has become two-layered in the context of IVF treatment— one is the responsibility of "failing" to conceive naturally that makes couples enter treatment; the other is the responsibility of "failed" treatment result. Fertility specialists practice strategic gendering—(un)gendering the two-layered responsibility—to manage the uncertainty of pregnancy. On the one hand, the discourse of "infertility solely as a female's problem" has been changed when patients are diagnosed with natural conception difficulty. Fertility specialists utilize statistics, the morphological image of sperm, and soft skills to tackle the social stigma of infertility during natural conception. On the other hand, females' responsibility has been subtly naturalized again through molecularization and genetization once couples enter IVF treatment. During the course of treatment, the gendered responsibility has shifted to the molecular/genetic level when the impact of advanced maternal age and the genetic material of egg on the treatment result is unevenly highlighted. In contrast, there is a missing discussion on males' genetic responsibility in the clinical context. Once the impact of sperm quality on fertilization is resolved through utilizing ICSI during IVF, the sperm is considered normal without concern of its genetic impact on the further development of the embryo and treatment result. This paper shows fertility specialists mediate the politics of reproductive responsibility, through which the knowledge of biological-determined "natural body," the difference of sex nature, and the gendered reproductive labor are reconfigured.

Session Organizer:

Dagoberto Cortez, The University of Texas at Austin

Chair:

Michael Halpin, Dalhousie University

347. Measurement and Commensuration in Professions, Session I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Quantification and commensuration have been major areas of inquiry in STS in recent years. STS work has highlighted the challenges of measuring the attributes or performance of individuals and of ensuring these measurements are comparable. While regulation and control through tracking has long been a feature of low-wage work, these new forms of quantification and commensuration are increasingly prevalent in high-status professional groups like physicians and nurses. Such forms of quantification and commensuration are often aimed at increasing productivity, agility, and well-being among professionals and occupational workers. They can also be used to assess, quantify and compare knowledge, skills, personal attributes, and emotional states, with the hope that developing measurements and quantifications will offer an alternative to traditional forms of evaluation, and that this might reduce bias in skill assessments. In this session we seek to explore how quantification and commensuration are remaking professional groups and identities, and how new quantification technologies may play a role in professionalizing projects.

Participants:

Inconsistent Quantification: A Mixed Methods Analysis of Gender Inequality in Emergency Medical Education
Alexandra E Brewer, University of Chicago; Laura Nelson, Northeastern University; Rebecca Ewert, University of Chicago; Anna Mueller, Indiana University

In 2013, emergency medicine (EM) adopted the Accreditation Council for Graduate Medical Education's (ACGME) Next Accreditation System (NAS), a nationally standardized framework for evaluating residents based on specialty-specific sub-competencies. The NAS relies heavily on quantification, requiring that attendings score resident performance numerically and that programs report these scores to the ACGME in order to maintain accreditation. Prior research suggests that the NAS may disadvantage women: although men and women receive similar scores at the beginning of EM residency, by the time of

graduation men's scores are significantly higher. In this paper, we build on prior findings by interrogating why attendings give male residents higher numerical scores than women residents. We combine qualitative, quantitative, and computational methods to analyze a dataset of 33,456 in-the-moment evaluations of residents by attendings that includes both numerical scores and textual comments, which provide some context into why a score was given. Our findings reveal that women receive more inconsistent evaluations than men across all three years of residency: their positive textual comments are more often accompanied by low numerical scores and vice versa. Based on these findings, we argue that evaluators use different processes to arrive at numerical scores for men and women in ways that reproduce gender inequality. Rather than standardizing resident evaluation, numerical scores may obfuscate biases in how attendings evaluate residents. These findings call into question the movement toward quantification in graduate medical education (which is considering moving to a competency-based graduation system) and in professional workplaces more generally.

Seeing Like a Situational Judgment Test *Alexandra Vinson, University of Michigan*

Situational Judgement Tests (SJTs) are commonly used in employment screening and have recently begun to be incorporated into the admissions requirements for health professions education programs in the U.S. These tests are designed to measure certain qualities of applicants, producing a quantified and commensurable score to assist in admissions decision-making. But how do these tests produce their measurements? What networks of practices can support the introduction and uptake of such a test into educational admissions? Taking as a case the Computer-based Assessment for Sampling Personal Characteristics (CASPer), I undertake an archaeology of the test, exploring discursive claims about what the test measures and how it produces those measurements, with the aim of understanding the realities such a test can bring into being.

The Value of Well-Being at Work: Health Professions and the Commensuration of Feelings *Kelly Underman, Drexel University*

Despite a rapid proliferation of interest in burnout among physicians and nurses and a flurry of initiatives proposed to foster 'well-being' instead (Brunsberg et al. 2019; National Academies of Medicine 2019), there is considerable debate among experts about how these concepts should be understood, measured, and intervened upon. Indeed, as hospital systems and medical schools increasingly devote resources to improving physician, nurse, and trainee well-being, what might be called a 'wellness industrial complex' has sprung up of conferences, workshops, consulting services, and even apps for fostering well-being and resilience among health professionals. This is in spite of much conceptual slippage between burnout and well-being in expert debates (Heinemann and Heinemann 2017). While well-being initiatives in workplaces date back to the 1980s with mixed 'success' (Conrad 1988; Kotarba and Bentley 1988), the kind of intensive focus that these initiatives are receiving today among health professionals is new. These efforts have intensified very recently, as health systems and educators struggle to deal with the ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic. This paper traces the rise of well-being discourse, the proliferation of expertise around well-being in the health professions, and explores the ways in which well-being is valued in healthcare—socially, politically, and economically.

What Is Academic Quality? The UK Research Excellence Framework As Situated Commensuration *Sveta Milyaeva, University of Bristol; Daniel Neyland, Goldsmiths, University of London*

In this paper we focus on the Research Excellence Framework

(REF) – the world’s longest standing system for competitive allocation of government research funding based on peer-review – and how it establishes discipline-neutral ‘academic quality’. Based on 38 semi-structured interviews with REF managers and academics across 36 REF assessment panels, we look into practices of commensuration as solving the problem of assessing a large set of seemingly incommensurable, heterogeneous, and not immediately apparent qualities of academic research outputs across various disciplines, from STEM to social sciences to humanities subjects. One key practice is calibration, which in STS has been considered a ‘test’ to boost the validity of scientific findings (Collins 1985), or an achievement in developing standards or ‘intercomparison of instruments’ (Mallard 1998). We show that in the case of the REF, calibration enables sets up situations (Boltanski and Thevenot 2006) that solve the problem of incommensurability by making diverse research outputs comparable locally. The situation requires academics to shift their mode of judgement from assessment (generalisation in a context of their respective ‘epistemic cultures’ (Knorr Cetina 1999)) to evaluation (narrowing peers’ vision through ascribing a value using a given scoring scale, thus focusing on the criteria, the rules, etc.). We argue that, alongside being consequential for academia, as it produces a questionable measure of academic quality, these situations are also important because they demonstrate how commensuration work achieves universality.

The Quantified Scholar: How Research Evaluations Transformed the British Social Sciences *Juan Pablo Pardo Guerra, UC San Diego*

This talk is based on my forthcoming book, *The Quantified Scholar*, where I study the effects of quantifying knowledge on the organization of disciplinary fields. Using a combination of qualitative, historical, and computational methods, I show that the introduction of standardized research evaluations to the British higher education system shaped local academic labor markets, fostering specific patterns of interinstitutional mobility that altered the epistemic diversity of social science disciplines and the organization of their academic fields. Much like a market-based intervention, research evaluations lead to a form of epistemic matching that has distinct consequences on how social scientific knowledge is generated in Britain today. In particular, when evaluations affect organizational units (such as academic departments) and stress disciplinary norms, they foster forms of isomorphism that lead to reductions in a discipline’s thematic diversity and a more homogeneous structure for the field.

Session Organizer:

Kelly Underman, Drexel University

Chair:

Alexandra Vinson, University of Michigan

348. What we talk about when we talk about depth – III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Recent scholarship on mining and drilling, urban infrastructure, maritime logistics, the transit of toxins, the anthropocene, and the disposal of bodies theorizes the politics of sub-surface worlds (Anand 2017, Appel et al. 2015, Campling & Colás 2021, Klinger 2017, Murphy 2013, Yusoff 2018). Bringing these depths into view has centered new spaces, scales, materials, and relations. Yet the concept of depth itself, and the responsibilities that attend its investigation, have not been sufficiently examined. Depth is more than a simple spatial signifier or linguistic trope. Thinking with and beyond verticality (Graham and Hewitt 2012), volumetric space (Weizman 2007, Elden 2013, Billé 2018), and metaphor (McKittrick 2018, Shalem 2017), we want to suggest that the deeps constitute a semiotic landscape that is resolutely material but always exceeds conventional materialist readings. Deep spaces matter: they are simultaneously material and meaningful. This panel engages critically and creatively with the mattering of chthonic landscapes, defined broadly. Encoded in the concept of depth are all kinds of latent associations and meanings. As such, we may speak of deep time, deep sleep, deep ecology, deep learning, the deep state, skin deep, diving

deep, depth of character, depth of perception, depth of field, depth of meaning, etc. How, we ask, are these (and many other) conceptualizations of depth tied to the deep places of the earth? And if, as Spivak teaches us, thought must be “written on the planet as planet” (2012: 349), how does thinking operate beneath the planetary surface?

Participants:

Humans Underground *Tamara Alvarez, Jagiellonian University*

Human bodies hide in the Earth’s deeps. Sometimes they lie just a few feet underground, covered by thin layers of sand and dust easily blown away by the wind. Others lie much deeper, in crypts and graves dig to bring those bodies closer to the divine or keep them out of sight. In paleoanthropology, the search for ancient human remains is also a search for deep time, when hominids struggled for survival and homo sapiens arose as a distinct, all-powerful species. These ancient humans, pieces of whom are found here and there in caves, deserts, and icy tundras, are bodies born before history was born, a time before politics. They allow the living to make universal, genetics-based claims about race, migration, and the species’ innate predatory relation to nature. Yet in many cases, these remains appear in subterranean spaces that conjure more recent and politically problematic histories. In this paper I discuss the simultaneous exhumation of cannibalized Neanderthals and executed civil war represaliados (enemies of the Francoist dictatorship) in the northern Spanish region of Asturias during the 2010s. What forms of expertise are enlisted to make sense of these bodies and speak in their name? In what ways do these remains force us to conceive of history as a past (dis)continuous with our present? What do the traces of atrocious violence left on these bodies tell us about the subterranean’s relation to death and collective memory?

Sensing and Seeing the Deep: Visualizing Underground Gold Mining Worlds *Sabine Luning, Leiden University; Robert Pijpers, University of Hamburg*

This paper addresses the relationship between depth and visibility in small-scale gold mining in West Africa. Our study of underground worlds, and how gold miners delve into them, foregrounds diversity and hybridity in knowledge, power and cosmological perspectives. Cultural paradigms stipulate possible ways of knowing the underground, qualities attributed to gold, and forms of wealth appropriation. Valuing the senses are key in such paradigms. Often small-scale gold miners attribute gold with agency: it has to allow miners to ‘see’ it. In capitalist, large-scale mining, gold is ‘seen’ quite differently. Histories of mining technologies describe how visualization and modeling changed the place of the senses in industrial underground extraction. Mapping underground minerals has become a professional activity aboveground, separated from the practices of extraction and direct sight and sensing of ore. Such visual, ‘scientific’ mediation of otherwise invisible deep worlds articulates with capitalist ‘speculation’. This paper analyses how, in our collaborative anthropological research with gold miners in Ghana, diverse ways of ‘sensing and seeing the deep’ worked in tandem as a consequence of the key role of visualization. Our verbal and visual communication was defined by a limitation: we, researchers, lacked the skills and courage to enter the deep, narrow spaces. Gold miners volunteered to film and photograph underground and engaged in drawing, and mapping aboveground to make us ‘see underground’. We analyse what this speculative research tells us about sensing the deep, the place of sight in accessing underground wealth, mediating deep knowledge, and the hybridity of cosmological perspectives.

Techniques of depth and the forensic truth *Pedro Telles da Silveira, Unicamp*

Questions of depth gained a new momentum with the so-called “forensic turn”. Mostly initiated in the mid-1980s, the forensic turn refers mainly to the application of forensic techniques in human rights investigations. While it has engaged with depth as a material practice, such as in the exhumation of corpses, recent

groups such as Forensic Architecture and the practice of digital archaeology have deployed media techniques to probe the underground and the unseen. Its regime of evidence goes beyond the visible, troubling the referentiality of traditional historical or juridical evidence. This evidence is constructed in the act of its technical perception. Metaphors of depth and shallowness have governed our relationship with digital media – for instance, in deep fakes. If, as Vilém Flusser argued, technical media bring a renewed shallowness to the world, which troubles the interpretive and critical act, what is to be done with the production of depth brought by these media operations deployed by forensics? Depth and shallowness are not fixed categories, but relative instances that mediate our relationship to the world. This paper studies the work of Forensic Architecture as an example of the troublesome but also productive usage of technical media to probe depth through technologies of visualization. It argues that these practices renew the meaning of the critical act by producing evidence and destabilizing both subject and object positions. Thus, while depth continues to be associated with truth, these truth claims are newly politicized through technical operations. Regarding depth, technics and politics enable each other.

Thinking Deep? Creative collaborations for Ungrounding thought *Harriet Hawkins, RHUL*

I begin, as many discussions of the deep do, from in the midst of its so-called ‘epistemological murk’. In asking ‘what lies beneath?’ the recent intensification of attention to going underground, under-sea and under-ice, has drawn to the fore the challenges the deep poses, not just as a site to think on or with, but as a locus which ‘un-grounds’ thought itself. As eyes and minds turn downward, this paper explores what creative research practices might offer to our thinking and talking about the deep. Exploring examples drawn from an ongoing collaboration with artist Flora Parrot, this paper visits a series of caves and tunnels. In doing so it probes the reoccurring tension between ‘solving’ the challenge of knowing the deep – of rendering it visible or otherwise sensible – and finding in its very unknowability, critical and political potential. Going ‘below’ with these creative practices I explore the role of sensing, imagining and speculation as integral to questions of ‘thinking deep’.

Session Organizers:

Anya Kaplan-Seem, University of Minnesota

Xander Lenc, University of California, Berkeley

Nicholas Anderman, University of California, Berkeley

Chair:

Anya Kaplan-Seem, University of Minnesota

349. Optical Media: The Impact of Visual Technologies - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Optical media, borrowed from Friedrich Kittler, is an expanded concept that connects photography, film and television with other techniques and technologies that mediate optics and vision (e.g. microscopes, telescopes, oscilloscopes, echocardiography, ad inf.). Normalized, expected and often desired, optical media shape how we perceive the reality that surrounds us, mediating our understanding and experience of our inter- and intra-relationships with ourselves, others, objects, and worlds. In so doing, they constitute power relationships that reify inequalities and uncertainties, the key themes of 4S 2021, rendering certain people, places, and things visible, invisible, or hypervisible. These issues have grown in importance in the wake of COVID-19 and social distancing, where optical media have become ubiquitous. This panel welcomes interdisciplinary research from STS and neighbouring fields that critically examine the role of these embedded and disruptive technologies in guiding our world views and relationships. By paying attention to the modes of seeing and looking that shape our perceptions, behaviours, and practices we can begin to better address their effects on other information systems including but not limited to the ones we work in, socialize in, and reside in. Questions we ask include how are modes of looking shaped by digital optical media? What

potentials are there for visual manipulation, exploitation, or psychological vulnerabilities? What new possibilities for ways of thinking, interacting or organizing information do these technologies offer? Who and what is being rendered visible, invisible, or hypervisible and the power politics of optical media?

Participants:

Construction of Optical Media to See "Nuchal Translucency"

Maiko Watanabe, Jichi Medical University

Obstetrics is a field, where optical media plays a major role in developing its expertise, for fetus, its object, is observable only through visual technology. What to see and not to see in fetus was defined by such optical media. This paper explores a case of nuchal translucency to understand the way in which obstetric mode of seeing is constructed. Nuchal translucency is the thin subcutaneous space observed at the back of fetal neck only during ultrasound scan provided in the early stage of pregnancy, specifically between 11th to 14th weeks of gestation. The space is commonly observed globally to gain the measurement of its width, which correlates with the possibility of fetus to have chromosome aneuploidy. To gain its accurate measurement, the fetus has to be observed from sagittal section. This thin space, which requires specific timing and posture for its observation, was discovered in 1992 by a British obstetrician, and quickly became the object of observation globally in the last decade of the 20th century. The paper explores the dynamic interaction of development in optical technology in obstetrics, progressed toward digitalization, “the modes of seeing” enabled by the technology shared among obstetric expertise, and the social condition that rationalized the visualization of the space, which welcomed another indicator for chromosome aneuploidy. This experience with nuchal translucency provides a good case to discuss the way in which our perception is constructed in the interaction of technology and social condition.

Experiencing Your Bodily Inside? *Simone Cecilie Grytter, CBMR and Medical Museion, University of Copenhagen*

Jose van Dijk argues that medical imaging technologies provide knowledge about health, and also affects our view of the body. This paper follows and expands this argument. It builds on ethnographic fieldwork at a Danish orthopedic surgery unit, where I observed arthroscopic surgeries of patients, who were awake and followed the procedure on a screen – thereby looking directly into their own interior. I argue that viewing inside the human body in-situ might affect a patient’s process of recovery, but also that patients might change how they understand their own body existentially. This mode of looking through technology alters patients’ understanding of their body - transforming it from a universal, mechanical body that either works or doesn’t work, to an individual body that belongs to the realm of nature, decaying biological tissue and uncertain futures. I follow Havi Carel’s notion that a change in a person’s body might lead to a change in their experience of the world, and argue that viewing inside our own human body might not only change the patient’s understanding of their own body, but also of the world. Finally, I engage critically with the act of looking, asking what is rendered visible (and what stays invisible), when we experience places through technology, which we otherwise could not experience – from our inner landscapes to the landscapes of Mars. This paper contributes to STS, by both staying true to the experiences of the patients, while also maintaining a critical eye on the ‘doings’ of imaging technology.

Seeing between: Imaging the Imperceptible in Molecular Representations of Aging and Age Intervention *Kirsten L Ellison, Trent University*

Efforts to see inside the body and to ‘image the unseen’ have a long history in science, medicine and imaging technology (Hentschel, 2014; Stafford, 1991). Technologies of visualization have afforded the once imperceptible object of the scientific/medical gaze an autonomy and mobility that it would

not usually have, allowing it to circulate beyond the walls of the clinic as an object of consumption, detached from the body within which it was once enclosed (Braidotti, 1994). In popular coverage of scientific and technological advancements in the field of anti-aging medicine, visual renderings of the inaccessible spaces of bodies, organs, blood vessels, cells, synapses, chromosomes, DNA helices, proteins, enzymes, and free radicals are frequently employed as insights into the molecular mechanisms and effects of biological aging. Building on a visual analysis of ‘molecular images’ pulled from over 200 online and print articles from a selection of popular science and technology magazines, I explore the discursive implications of seeing the unseen. Drawing on Carusi and Hoel’s (2014; Hoel & Carusi, 2015) re-theorization of the ‘measuring body’, I argue that these images function as multidimensional measures of being that demand and enact a new corporeal sensibility – a seeing between – one that is constituted in the movement from outer to inner, whole to part, organ to molecule. Although this paper focuses on the aging body, this is a corporeal sensibility that impacts all aspects of our biological lives and one that has particular relevance to the visual landscape that currently surrounds the COVID-19 pandemic.

Do Artifacts Prevent Politics? Artisanal Logics of Harm Reduction *Nancy D. Campbell, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute*

Fentanyl Test Strips (FTS) allow rapid visual determinations of whether or not fentanyl is present. As artifacts made to signify overdose death prevention, FTS enact ‘good relations’ other than those for which they were developed and licensed. This paper contributes to socio-material theorization of harm reduction in relation to the agency, empowerment, and liveliness of drug users through co-creation via off-label use. The socio-materialities of FTS offer new renderings of facticity and artifactuality. Originating in Toronto, FTS were creatively deployed in Vancouver before being piloted in the United States. As border-crossing and boundary-hopping artifacts, FTS were once ‘technologies of suspicion,’ now used as ‘technologies of solidarity’. This paper contextualizes FTS within drug control, overdose prevention, and harm reduction in North America. In Boaventura de Sousa Santos’ terms (2018), the ‘artisanal logics’ by which FTS were neither mechanical nor predictable; while “processes, tools, and materials impose some conditions, . . . they leave leeway for a significant margin of freedom and creativity. The truth is that the political work underlying the articulations between struggles, when under the epistemologies of the South, has many affinities with artisanal work” (de Sousa Santos, 2018, p. 35). The creative political craft that dovetails harm reduction with other struggles occurs through materially grounded ‘good relations’ and practices. Rethinking the socio-materiality of harm reduction through artisanal practices in relation to decolonial epistemologies of the global South, this paper sets out to think ‘facts’, ‘artifacts,’ and Fentanyl Test Strips together.

Session Organizers:

Paula Sanchez Nunez de Villavicencio, University of Toronto
Alexander Monea, George Mason University

350. Corona Truth Wars: Testing and Contesting Knowledge in a Hyper-Mobile Pandemic - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic created a global crisis challenging humankind to develop as quickly as possible reliable knowledge about the virus and its devastating effects on our bodies and societies in order to minimize such harms. This situation of great uncertainty and enormous stakes incited a historically unique international knowledge producing effort by institutionalized scientists and research groups. While debate and disagreement exists within these scientific communities, more controversial are the various competing “outside” forms and sources of information on the virus and its mitigation strategies. Some are clear disinformation

campaigns or far-fetched conspiracy theories, others are legitimate challenges to the temporary status quo. In the hyper-mobile context of knowledge production during an evolving pandemic, it is often hard to tell the difference. Questions such as ‘what information is reliable?’, ‘which experts should we follow?’, and ‘what (epistemic) authorities are to trust?’, take center stage in public debates. Prevalent clear-cut distinctions between “real” knowledge controversies and “fake” disruptions of scientific progress obscure the fact that the global quest for truthful knowledge about the virus is entangled with various (geo)political dynamics, government policy pressures, media reporting, platform moderation and public understandings of it all. STS scholars are perfectly equipped with concepts, theories and methods to help understand these complex dynamics involving uncertainty, changing insights, and (covert) manipulation. In this panel we invite scholars working on such “corona truth wars”: we welcome both empirical and theoretical studies on the cultures, politics and technologies of today’s corona knowledge contestations.

Participants:

Hinge Objects and Boundary Objects in the Corona Truth Wars: Studying Masks and Vaccines *Ana Cosima Rughinis, University of Bucharest; Michael G. Flaherty, Eckerd College*

The Covid-19 pandemic has mobilized two broad alliances in support of conflicting worldviews. The Corona-anxious alliance has advanced the novel coronavirus as the main reason for concern, and has advocated pandemic-control measures, including masks, lockdowns, and widespread vaccination. The Corona-skeptical alliance has advanced an antipodal combination of beliefs, including some, if not all, of the following: denying the seriousness of the pandemic, pointing to elite manipulation as the true enemy of the population, and representing masks and vaccines as harmful and/or futile interventions. We discuss masks and vaccines as instances of “hinge objects”, a concept that we derive from “boundary objects” (Star and Griesemer 1989, Star 2010). Social actors make use of interpretively flexible boundary objects to collaborate without consensus (ibid.), and they make use of interpretively flexible hinge objects to systematically construct opposing worlds. Hinge objects articulate antipodal worldviews in key points that make possible the circulation and conversion of evidence. We argue that a close examination of the symmetrical, obverse construction of masks and vaccines in such polar worldviews allows us to overcome the stubborn deficit model (Gross 1994), which remains a popular explanation of science denial in multiple fields. Thus, we discuss and illustrate symmetrical acts of science-work or staging science (Degele 2005), number work or quantification (Espeland and Stevens 2009), time work (Flaherty 2003, 2011), emotion work (Hochschild 1979), and boundary maintenance (Lamont and Molnár 2002) in the construction of hinge objects and the articulation of bifurcated realities.

Post-truth or pre-truth? Laymen and scientists confronted with face masks *Franck Cochoy, Université Toulouse Jean-Jaurès - LISST-CERS; Madeleine Akrich, Centre de Sociologie de l’Innovation-i3 – Mines Paristech PSL University*

In recent years, much attention has been focused on post-truth (Parasia, 2017), “fake news” (Molina et al., 2019; Allen et al., 2020), and conspiracy theories of all kinds (Bronner, 2013). The questioning of objective knowledge obviously undermines the very foundations of pluralist debate and democracy. However, do all current challenges in terms of knowledge pertain to post-truth? Is this notion well suited to life in an uncertain world (Callon, Barthes and Lascoumes, 2001; Akrich and Méadel, 2007), where the stakes are not those of the post-truth, for the good reason that the truth is not known, but has yet to be established? Wouldn't it be better to symmetrize the reflection, by completing the examination of the post-truth with a questioning of the pre-truth, that is to say, of the scholarly and secular approaches that aim, independently or jointly, to take into account and remove uncertainties? We propose to address these

questions based on the case of the pandemic crisis, and more specifically on the controversies that have surrounded the use of face masks (Cochoy, 2020). In order to assess the "post-truth" and "pre-truth" dynamics that are unfolding in the face of masks, we will mobilize a large corpus of press articles published in 2020 and readers comments about these articles. What our survey shows is that, people do not simply affirm opinions; they also express aloud a large number of uncertainties. Thus, it is perhaps only by supplementing the monitoring of post-truth with the examination of pre-truth that we might find the means to develop new certainties and, ideally, to re-establish the conditions for a life without masks, a common meaning and a common world.

“Solving for Q: Slow Disaster and Conspiracy in the COVID-19 Era” *Scott Knowles, KAIST (Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology)*

On January 6, 2021 when insurrectionists charged into the United States Capitol Building with the intention of taking over the Electoral College process and installing Donald Trump as a re-elected President, their ranks included an array of white nationalists, militia members, disinformation practitioners, and QAnon adherents. Taken separately, the action was a startling, but predicted, climax to a Presidency in which Trump retweeted and speechified QAnon-friendly conspiracy theories and disinformation almost every day. Combined with the broader uncertainty and anger of the COVID-19 pandemic, the January 6 insurrection offers a deeper insight into the ways that conspiracy theory and disaster combine to multiply their separate impacts. Until only recently, disaster researchers treated conspiracy theories like the World Trade Center “inside job” theory or the Sandy Hook shooting “false flag” operation as epiphenomena: interesting but largely unrelated to the causal chain provoking the core event. An enormously creative and dedicated group of scholars including researchers at the Shorenstein Center of Media, Politics, and Public Policy (Harvard) and the University of Washington’s Center for an Informed Public found themselves thrust into the role as instant explainers of the conspiracy pandemic that accompanied the COVID-19 pandemic. Their work was essential in providing a deeper context and causality—explaining that the wide variety of COVID disinformation and conspiracy was connected to well-prepared actors bent on disrupting the US political system, and/or advancing well-established agendas of white nationalism, anti-vaccination/anti-science politics, or anti-Democratic party action, to name just a few. This paper picks up with the compound January 6 COVID-QAnon disaster connection—but solving for the power of Q requires an analytical move that takes us into a slow disaster frame. We cannot determine the impact of conspiracy on an individual disaster event, unless we search out the deeper structural connections between conspiracy theorists and the processes that made the pandemic itself possible. In this slow disaster mindset we look for the inter-relationships among conspiracy and disaster, noting the ways that over time what were once wild fantasies become more and more central to the explanatory discourse around disaster itself.

Borderlands between science, propaganda and conspiracy: A content analysis of mainstream media coverage of 5G and health concerns during the COVID-19 pandemic in USA, UK and France *Kevin Bardosh*

This paper explores media representations in the USA, UK and France related to 5G wireless radiation and human health concerns during the COVID-19 pandemic in 2020. In particular, I present the results of a content analysis conducted on a compiled database of > 800 mainstream news articles that cover the 12-months of 2020. This was a particularly complex time, as 5G infrastructures were being rolled-out around the globe in parallel to various conspiracy theories circulating about the relationship between 5G and the COVID-19 pandemic. I explore how the media, as part of the emerging field of “infodemiology”,

attempted to “debunk” such popular conspiracy theories. However I also question the accuracy of such efforts in light of long-standing scientific uncertainties and the contested politics of knowledge in the RF-EMF field. The paper will raise a number of questions about the field of infodemiology, media representations of 5G in the new digital ecosystem, the framing of public anxieties and concerns, and the influence of telecom corporations and lobbying groups. I will also explore and critique the work of social scientists that have published in this area. Lastly, my analysis will reveal interesting differences between the Anglophone (USA and UK) and Francophone (France) media coverage of 5G and health. I will discuss some possible reasons for this.

Session Organizers:

Jaron Harambam, Institute for Media Studies - KU Leuven
Ehler Voss, University of Siegen

Discussant:

Linsey Jane McGoey

351. Genealogies of the Human in AI Systems III.

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

From rational actors to addicted users, Eurocentric theories of mind and society inform the design of AI/ML systems, both explicitly and through uninterrogated universalising norms and assumptions. Scholarly work has examined the societal impacts of AI systems, but less has been done to examine the assumptions of the social that inform such systems. This panel explores a genealogy of the human in the machine, examining AI systems as a palimpsest of conceptions of mind and society inherited from the fields that feed into AI research including cognitive science, behavioural psychology, economics, and philosophy. We seek to tease apart the models and paradigms of the human that are translated into code, used to act on, navigate, categorise and govern the world. Hubert Dreyfus famously drew on phenomenology to challenge the rationalist assumptions of human intelligence underlying AI research. “Facts and rules”-based theories of intelligence have given way to a neural network paradigm, responding in part to Dreyfus’ challenge. Yet the question of what notions of the human are entangled in AI systems remains—calling us to examine not only conceptions of human intelligence—but also human bodies and human social structures. We invite papers examining how paradigms of mind and society are explicitly encoded, invisibly inscribed, and entirely omitted from AI/ML design and exploring the consequences of these encodings and erasures. We are particularly interested in work exploring AI systems as situated in racial capitalism and colonialism and the racialised and gendered dimension of the human as encoded in AI systems.

Participants:

Disrupting Eurocentric Genealogies of Human Autonomy in AI
Eleanor DRAGE, The University of Cambridge

The European Union Scientific Foresight Unit’s 2020 report “Artificial intelligence: How does it work, why does it matter and what can we do about it?”, dedicates a section to the possibility of AI diminishing “human autonomy” (40). The report’s emphasis on the potential “erosion” of human autonomy, if we become over-reliant on AI, expresses transhumanist assessments of existential risk, for example in the work of Nick Bostrom and Sandra Wachter, who frame the protection of human autonomy as an AI safety issue. This implies that humans are by nature autonomous beings, that is, that we have the capacity for thought and action independent of other forces and entities. As is evidenced by the above example, this Enlightenment-inherited assumption is beginning to pass from transhumanist doctrine to international policy recommendations and legislation. This paper draws on intersectional feminist scholarship to present the following arguments against the use of ‘autonomy’ as a way of conceptualising human agency in relation to AI on the following grounds: 1) the term obscures how all humans are already dependent on infrastructural support in order to exercise agency (Judith Butler, Hannah Arendt); 2) it is encoded in

Enlightenment-based doctrine, which made the subordination of women and indigenous peoples the condition for European sovereignty (Sylvia Wynter); 3) it obscures how AI denies agency to groups most affected by existing structural inequality (Safiya Noble); and 4) it pertains to a lexical field that promotes human separatism over co-existence and inter-relationality with non-human life forms (Jane Bennett, Karen Barad).

Genealogies of Diagnostic Assemblages: Shaping a

Radiological Sense *Flora Lysen, Maastricht University; Sally Wyatt, Faculty of Arts and Social Sciences, Maastricht Univer*

“Radiologists will lose their jobs to AI,” is by now commonplace in media reporting on the future of health care. In turn, STS researchers have urged to study automation practices not as replacement but as displacement, calling for a careful examination of new configurations of human labour and (automated) technical systems. This paper examines changing relationships between radiologists, engineers and computer scientists, focusing on how the work of the radiologist has been envisioned in relation to, as well as in competition with, emerging (automatization) technologies. Drawing on historical sources from the 1950s until the present, in the U.S. and Europe, we demonstrate how the core work of the radiologist was increasingly imagined as a combined visual detection and pattern recognition task. We claim that the emergence of new technical systems and concepts (such as the notion of “visual scanning” and “image interpreter systems”), tied to novel human-factors and psychophysiological research, helped shape a new conception of a radiological sense, that is, of the disciplined and distributed perception of radiologists and technologists. Tracing these genealogies of human-machine configurations in radiology (as diagnostic assemblages) helps us to understand current debates about AI and pattern recognition in image-based medicine based on shifting notions of “seeing” and “recognizing” patterns. This genealogical study is part of a bigger project (situated in the Netherlands) about AI in image-based clinical decision making.

On the Contesting Conceptualization of the Human Subject:

Between ‘Homo-Microbis’ and ‘Homo-Algorithmicus’ *Dan M. Kotliar, Department of Communication, Stanford University; Rafi Groszlik, Ben Gurion University of the Negev & Beit Berl*

In the last two decades, the study of human microbiota – the vast microbial communities in and around the human body – has highlighted human and microbial interdependency and co-evolution, thus offering a radical epistemic and ontological shift from the individualistic, modernistic view of the human subject (Gilbert, Sapp, and Tauber 2012, 326). Research has accordingly offered to see humans as “homo-microbis” (Helmreich 2014), or “holobionts” – complex biomolecular networks composed of a human host and its associated microbes (Bordenstein and Theis 2015). But what happens to this shift when it gets commodified? Based on an ethnographic account of a prominent scientific research project that offers a microbiome-based personalized nutrition, and of the successful start-up that emerged from it, this article examines the popularization and commodification of the microbiome, and the ensuing constitution of the human subject. We show that in its commodification, the microbiome is acknowledged, but it is also paradoxically seen as a data-driven, individuating marker that does not question humans’ individuality, but rather, highlights it. We further argue that this view necessarily depends on opaque machine learning algorithms that produce a quantified self – a supra-human, neoliberal agent who relies on meticulous self-tracking. We accordingly show that the homo-microbis is also a homo-algorithmicus – a being that can only access its own nonhuman sub-parts by blindly following opaque algorithmic recommendations on an app. Thus, we show that the ontological turn offered by microbiome research which is

highly dependent on cultural, economic, and technological determinants, and is accordingly shaped by them.

Programming what futures? A rhetorical analysis of an AI textbook *Levin Kim, The Information School, University of Washington*

As an influential textbook on AI, Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach (AIMA) presents “key ideas that have emerged over the past fifty years of AI” to convince students that AI is “a subject most worthy of study” (Russell and Norvig, 2010). Understanding gender and technology as concepts constructed and reified through repeated interactions (Adam 1998), this project draws attention to the broader implications of the metaphors (e.g. cartography, childrearing) that the authors invoke in this process. In particular, three aspects of AIMA’s account of AI history are pulled into focus: (1) positioning AI as a universal field, (2) the history of AI constructed a kind of bildungsroman, and (3) the limited ways of knowing recognized in discourses of AI. Building on work examining the rhetorical construction of “what AI stays it does, and how it says it does” (Hunter 1991), this project takes a feminist STS approach to rhetorically analyzing the stories that AI researchers tell about their field. This surfaces hidden ways of thinking that computer scientists rely on to construct AI’s “scientific folklore” (Lessl, 1999), as these embedded metaphors have explicitly shaped (and continue to shape) how AI researchers orient themselves to their subject of study. More broadly, it sheds light on how the limited ways of thinking about artificiality, intelligence, human-ness become fixed within the field. These metaphors, and the structures of power that they invoke, underscore how gender, race, and power are inextricably intertwined with AI’s history, present, and future. References Stuart J. Russell, Peter Norvig, and Ernest Davis, Artificial Intelligence: A Modern Approach, 3rd ed, Prentice Hall Series in Artificial Intelligence (Upper Saddle River: Prentice Hall, 2010). Alison Adam. 1998. Artificial Knowing: Gender and the Thinking Machine. Taylor and Francis, Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9780203005057>. Lynette Hunter, “Rhetoric and Artificial Intelligence,” *Rhetorica* 9, no. 4 (November 1991): 317–40, <https://doi.org/10.1525/rh.1991.9.4.317>. Thomas M. Lessl, “The Galileo Legend as Scientific Folklore,” *Quarterly Journal of Speech* 85, no. 2 (May 1999): 146–68, <https://doi.org/10.1080/00335639909384251>.

Rediscovering the human in AI design for fairness *Ana Carolina Nunes, Oregon State University; Shaozeng Zhang, Oregon State University*

This paper is an initial report of our fair AI design project by a small research team made up of anthropologists and computer scientists. Our collaborative project was developed in response to the recent debates on AI’s ethical and social issues (Elish and boyd 2018). We share this understanding that “numbers don’t speak for themselves,” but data enter into research projects already “fully cooked” (D’Ignazio and Klein 2020). Therefore, we take an anthropological approach to observing, recording, understanding, and reflecting upon the process of machine learning algorithm design since the first steps of choosing and coding datasets for training and building algorithms. We tease apart the encoding of social-cultural paradigms in the generation and use of datasets in algorithm design and testing. By doing so, we rediscover the human in data to challenge the methodological and social assumptions in data use and then to adjust the model and parameters of our algorithms. This paper centers on tracing the social trajectory of the Correctional Offender Management Profiling for Alternative Sanctions, known as the COMPAS dataset. This dataset contains data of over 10,000 criminal defendants in Broward County in Florida, the U.S. Since its publication, it has become a landmark dataset in the study of algorithmic fairness and was also used to design and train our algorithm for recidivism prediction. This paper presents our observation that data results from a complex set of social,

political, and historical assumptions and circumstances and demonstrates how the social trajectory of data can be taken into the design of AI as automated systems become more intricate into our daily lives.

Speaking Their Minds: Language as Thought in AI Past and Present *Evan Donahue*

The field of artificial intelligence (AI) emerged in the mid 1950s against a wider backdrop of cybernetic conversations surrounding intelligent machines. Growing out of wartime codebreaking work at Blechley park, the processing of language using digital computers offered an immediate and irresistible metaphor for early AI researchers, predicated as it was on a long history of associating language and thought in western thought. As would often be noted in this early moment, although "thought" was the ultimate aim, the field would simply have to make do with studying language until thought was better understood. Although the definition of machine "thought" has evolved, its tacit connection with language remains, as suggested by the recent remark of a prominent AI researcher at a major industrial laboratory that, "language is an imperfect, incomplete, and low-bandwidth serialization protocol for the internal data structures we call thoughts." In this talk, I trace the history and consequences of AI's insistence on treating language and thought as synonymous. As I argue, by imagining language to be an outgrowth of an inevitable genetic endowment of the human race rather than a set of practices for navigating spaces shared by human, animal, and machine, current AI research on language often applies too narrow a standard for what counts as language. This narrowness frustrates researchers when ubiquitous communicative behaviors remain forever out of their systems' reach, and carries serious social consequences when those machines are applied to analyze and regulate the shared public spaces of digital discourse.

Session Organizer:

Alexa Hagerty, University of Cambridge

Chair:

Siri Lamoureux, University of Siegen, Germany

352. Same Same but Different: Race and Racializations across National, Disciplinary and Temporal Contexts - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

In human diversity research, race is a moving target. It is rarely clearly defined, and takes on different meanings and labels in different contexts, and often reveals itself as racialized connotations of other terms. From an international perspective, it is apparent that while race is used in political and scientific contexts in the USA or Brazil, for example, in continental Europe, by contrast, today it is commonly considered a taboo. This difference is partly rooted in divergent conceptual meanings in different languages, and various political as well as scientific strategies for dealing with the historical burden of the concept. However, even in countries that are largely imagined as post-racial, race remains as an "absent presence" (M'charek/Schramm/Skinner 2014) within other terms in use such as "ethnicity", "population", "migrant background", "biogeographical ancestry", "metapopulation" etc. In this panel we welcome contributions inquiring into the national, disciplinary and/or temporal specifics of human difference categorizations – with a focus on, but not limited to, the life sciences. We are particularly interested in the shaping of processes of categorization and in the continuity and discontinuity of concepts of group classification across/in different contexts and specific situations.

Participants:

Different Kinds Of Blackness? On Brazilian Attempts To Define The Target Group Of Affirmative Action *Sarah Lempp*, University of Bayreuth

Since 2014, there are affirmative action policies for Afro-Brazilians in Brazil's public service. The law establishing these policies defines 'negros' as their legitimate target group and specifies this term as "those who self-declared as pretos [black]

or pardos [brown] in the application process". The amalgamation of these two categories is common in Brazilian statistics and was advocated by the Brazilian Black movement for a long time. However, in the context of affirmative action and with reference to the famous narrative of Brazil as a country with a high degree of 'racial mixture', there is a common argument nowadays that the majority of the Brazilian population could count as pardo – and that therefore not all pardos should be entitled to affirmative action. Accordingly, there are heated debates around supposed cases of 'fraud' – i.e. people who 'unrightfully' applied for a quota vacancy –, with those accused usually being defined or self-defining as pardos. By drawing on ethnographic research as well as on press reports and juridical documents, this paper examines the debate around such cases accused of 'fraud' and the related attempts to define the legitimate target group of the quota policies. Which kind of 'blackness' is enacted in these attempts? What counts as 'fraud'? And what does this tell us about race as a category of difference and as an administrative indicator? By discussing these questions, the paper sheds light on the enactment of racialized categories in a very specific context and thus contributes to STS research analyzing human difference classification.

What personalisation can do for you!; Or, how to do racial discrimination without "race" *Thao Phan*, Monash University; *Scott Wark*, University of Warwick

Between 2016 and 2020, Facebook allowed advertisers in the United States to target their advertisements using three broad "ethnic affinity" categories: "African American," "U.S.-Hispanic," and "Asian American." Superficially, these categories were supposed to allow advertisers to target demographic groups without using data about users' race, which Facebook explicitly does not collect. This paper uses the life and death of these "ethnic affinity" categories to argue that they exemplify a novel mode of racialisation made possible by machine learning techniques. Adopting Wendy H. K. Chun's conceptualisation of race "and/as" technology as an analytical frame, this paper focuses on what these categories use race to do. These categories worked by analysing users' preferences and behaviour: they were supposed to capture an "affinity" for a broad demographic group, rather than registering membership of that group. That is, they were supposed to allow advertisers to "personalise" content for users depending on behaviourally determined affinities. We argue that, in effect, Facebook's ethnic affinity categories were supposed to operationalise a "post-racial" mode of categorising users. But the paradox of personalisation is that in order to apprehend users as individuals, platforms must first assemble them into groups based on their likenesses with other individuals. This paper uses an analysis of these categories to argue that even in the absence of data on a user's race—even after the demise of the categories themselves—users can still be subject to techniques of inclusion or exclusion for discriminatory ends.

Around the R***-word. Debates in and beyond Switzerland *Anne Lavanchy*, Applied University Western Switzerland

My communication aims at highlighting how debates about the translation of "race" and race-related concepts in a publication project joining French- and German-speaking academics (Dos Santos et al., forthcoming) can contribute to foster decolonial approaches of racialisation. Gathering several scholars analysing race-related issues in the historical and current Swiss society, the objective of the edited volumes is to give an account of race research in a national context where race is both a linguistic taboo and an absent presence. Dominant whiteness narratives have long pictured Switzerland as an innocent and virtuous nation having stayed aside from colonial endeavour, and, thus, from racialised inequalities – as illustrated by the framing of racially marked bodies as non-nationals (Lavanchy 2015; 2020). Challenges posed by the translation of the R***-word into French and German have been heatedly discussed amongst the seven editors, crystallised around two main issues: what is the

best way to show the presence of racial thinking through the production of body markers? How can we name such processes both acknowledging the burden of classical, evolutionist race representation and avoiding the pitfalls of legitimating racialized categorization (Guillaumin 1981)? Through the analysis of these debates, in particular about the difficulty to translate expression such as PoC, Whiteness or Race into German, my paper critically considers the use of English as dominant scientific language, thus pleading for the necessity to decenter critical race studies through provincialization.

Race and Rasse: Comparing Conceptions of Race in Germany and the United States. *Daniel James, Heinrich Heine University; Leda Berio, Heinrich Heine University; Benedict Kenyah-Dampety, Heinrich-Heine-University Düsseldorf*

In this talk, we offer a comparative empirical analysis of race conceptions in the US and Germany. A central problem with extant accounts of the ordinary concept of race is that these analyses are restricted to the US-context. Accordingly, Hardimon (2003) suggested a single, 'logical core' to the ordinary concept of race that applies globally. Recently, Ludwig (2019) has challenged this idea, citing the striking differences between the US and Germany, which have become particularly salient as the German Federal Government pushes to replace the term "Rasse" in German Basic Law. Ludwig suggests several different conceptions (rather than the concept) of race to account for strong and partial cross-cultural (dis-)continuities between them. However, this analysis is still in need of more robust empirical support. In our talk, we will address this lacuna. First, we investigate potential differences in the use of the words "race" and "Rasse" through a comparative corpus analysis. Second, following the methodology in Shulman et al. (2009) and Machery and Faucher (2020), we experimentally test whether those differences in use correspond to differences in assigning race membership. In an online experiment, US-American and German speakers are asked to assign racial membership for several fictive persons who systematically differed in the features identified in the first study (and other potentially important factors for racial membership discussed in the literature, such as visual features, geographical origin, genetic makeup, nationality, and ethnicity/religion). This allows us to identify and, in particular, compare the American and German conceptions of race.

Session Organizers:

Thiago Pinto Barbosa, Universität Bayreuth
Nils Ellebrecht, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany
Veronika Lipphardt, Albert-Ludwigs-Universität Freiburg, University College Freiburg

Chairs:

Tino Pluemecke, Institute for Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany
Andrea zur Nieden, Institute of Sociology, University of Freiburg, Germany

Discussants:

Mihai Surdu, Research Centre on Antigypsyism/Forschungsstelle Antiziganismus
Jenny Reardon, UC Santa Cruz

353. Ways of Healing: Exploring non-Biomedical Cures as Emancipatory and Biopolitical Knowledge-Practices - I: Pluralism and difference in non-biomedical healing and wellbeing

11:30 to 1:00 pm
4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Participants:

Revitalising more-than-biomedical healing through the 4th Tier

Coll de Lima Hutchison, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine; Andrea Núñez Casal, University of Oxford, UK; Mahesh Mathpati, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine; John Porter, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine

Local health traditions have largely been devalued in health care systems that depend on biomedical understandings of health and disease. Such health care systems fail to recognise that a population can be 'self-reliant' in its health care practices and philosophy; a perspective that is latent within non-Western health cultures, such as the ancient Asian tradition of Ayurveda (Mathpati et al., 2020). We draw on our research and lived experiences with Ayurveda, Movement/Meditation practices and Galician Curanderism (local healing practices from the Northwest of Spain, including the preparation of fermented foods and beverages) to experiment and speculate on how attention to embodied knowledge-practices can help revitalise our individual and collective capacities for more-than-biomedical healing. We situate these practices in relation to our proposal for an additional tier in health care, the '4th tier': 'a community owned and managed strategy for self-help in health care services, that has the potential when created effectively, to reduce the dependence [...] on the three institutionalised tiers of conventional health care systems, which are delivered by health care professionals, drugs and devices and managed by the Government and private sector' (Mathpati et al., 2020). We reflect on how the 4th tier lays the theoretical ground for connecting 'new' practices of embodied (self) care and engaged research through which lay expertise and lived experiences are valued alongside biomedical and social sciences research to reconfigure problems and generate collective outcomes.

Well-being in Ayurveda and ecological sustainability *Pushya A Gautama*

Nodal Ayurveda texts emphasize, when discussing well-being, that the human is not the centre of the world, but one strand of a much larger, living breathing cosmos. One of the terms often used in the context of well-being in Ayurveda is 'samatva', or balance. Well-being, in Ayurvedic thought, is understood as the discovery of a dynamic balance between the body (śarīra), mind (manas) and the ecosystem (loka). The current work will attempt to critically examine an Ayurvedic understanding of well-being with particular focus on its implications for ecological sustainability. In stark contrast to Western Cartesian reductionist approaches to health, that isolate well-being from nature, Ayurveda contextualizes well-being in nature and the earth, and considers the human being as a microcosm of the larger earth macrocosm (loka- puruṣa - sāmāya). Ayurvedic notions of wellness, illness, medicines, therapies, lifestyles, diets and sociocultural practices have all emerged around this understanding of fundamental interconnectedness between the individual and his/her ecosystem. This paper will also attempt to understand how this worldview translates into lived practices, and examines how these may inform a more holistic redefinition of health as we contemplate a newly post-pandemic world.

Exploring Universals Among Medical Systems *Claire M. Cassidy, Windpath Healing Works*

In the United States today, we have many medical choices, but one system is so dominant that others are difficult to access. Given that biomedicine has been widely criticized for its material focus, high cost, corporate attachment, and lack of humane care, we may wonder why things haven't changed, why other options haven't been more widely accepted. One reason is that once you are ensconced within a medical model, especially if dominant, it can be hard to think beyond it. I wish to break that log-jam. My 'way-in' is to examine the concept of 'different,' often interpreted as 'worse,' and find ways in which 'difference' can be plumbed for its positive potential to serve. One approach is to find the commonalities—the Universals—that underlie

'difference.' Then differences can be seen as outgrowths of varying interpretations of the universals, which should improve neutrality in observation; out of this we might be able to move toward creating a functional plural medical system. Here I identify 3 philosophical universals that underlie all the many medical explanatory models of existing Medicines, and one surprising practice universal—vibration—that links every medical interventive technique in the world. Presently there is growing awareness of the limitations of the reductionistic ordinary, and a growing urge to reframe thinking toward complexity. Recognizing universals, and being able to reframe 'difference' as ordinary, is part of that task, and a fruitful way to move toward accepting Medicines other than biomedicine as valid, powerful, and useful.

Medical Pluralism: Equitable Mosaic Rather Than Homogenised Composite *Kunhi Lakshmi Josyula, The George Institute for Global Health*

Allopathy or Western medicine is the mainstream system of medicine in most of the world, and exerts hegemony over myriad traditional, complementary, and alternative systems of medicine (TCAM), and local health traditions (LHT). Nevertheless, non-allopathic systems of medicine, indigenous or adopted, are part of all cultures: Medical pluralism is yesterday's, today's, and tomorrow's reality. However, pluralistic health systems seldom view different systems of medicine with an egalitarian lens. Allopathy occupies the mainstream, TCAM systems come lower in hierarchy, and LHT are frequently overlooked as systems of health. Numerous non-allopathic systems of medicine are denied their individuality. While there is a consciousness that diverse systems of medicine should be conserved, the goals in the establishment of a pluralistic health system fall far short of accomplishment, with implications for the health workforce, service delivery, and leadership and governance [1]. The history of pluralistic health systems [2,3] is too often one of unequal political power, philosophical hegemonies, and inequitable inclusion of non-allopathic systems of medicine. "Integration" may be implemented by reductive pruning of various systems of medicine [4] and the force-fitting of disparate elements into a combination to address particular population health concerns. In non-integrative pluralistic contexts, the different systems of medicine are often reported to languish in uneasy, unproductive co-existence [5-7]. Foundational requirements for an equitable, productive, vibrant pluralistic health system are mutual awareness and respect among proponents of the diverse systems of medicine. The systems of medicine need to be treated as dynamic, interacting social systems, an equitable mosaic rather than a homogenised composite. References: 1. World Health Organization (2007) Everybody's business: Strengthening health systems to improve health outcomes. WHO's framework for action. Geneva: World Health Organization; 2007.

http://www.who.int/healthsystems/strategy/everybodys_business.pdf. Accessed May 24, 2018 2. Josyula K, Lakshmi, Devaki Nambiar, Venkatesh Narayan, T. N. Sathyanarayana, John Porter, and Kabir Sheikh. Cultural consonance, constructions of science, and co-existence: A review of the integration of traditional, complementary, and alternative medicine in low- and middle-income countries. *Health Policy and Planning*. 2015 Oct;30(8):1067-77. doi: 10.1093/heapol/czu096. 3. Sheikh K, Josyula LK, Zhang X, Bigdeli M, Ahmed SM. Governing the mixed health workforce: learning from Asian experiences. *BMJ Global Health* 2017;2:e000267. doi:10.1136/bmjgh-2016-000267 4. Lakshmi J. K. (2020) Consonances and dissonances: ancient Ayurveda and contemporary Ayurvedic clinical practice. *Indian J Med Ethics*. Jul-Sep; 5(3) NS: 250-2. DOI: 10.20529/IJME.2020.082. 5. D. Nambiar, V. V. Narayan, L. K. Josyula, J. D. H. Porter, T. N. Sathyanarayana, K. Sheikh. Experiences and meanings of integration of TCAM (Traditional, Complementary and Alternative Medical) providers in three Indian states: Results

from a cross-sectional, qualitative implementation research study. *BMJ Open* 2014; 4:e005203 doi:10.1136/bmjopen-2014-005203 6. K. Lakshmi Josyula, Kabir Sheikh, Devaki Nambiar, Venkatesh V. Narayan, T.N. Sathyanarayana, John D. H. Porter. "Getting the water-carrier to light the lamps": Discrepant role perceptions of traditional, complementary, and alternative medical practitioners in government health facilities in India. *Social Science and Medicine*, Vol 166: 214-222. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1016/j.socscimed.2016.08.038> 7. Lakshmi, JK (2012) Less equal than others? Experiences of AYUSH medical officers in primary health centres in Andhra Pradesh. *Indian Journal of Medical Ethics*.IX(1):18-21.

Session Organizer:

Andrea Núñez Casal, University of Oxford, UK

Chair:

John Porter, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine

Discussant:

Mahesh Mathpati, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine

354. Biometrics on the Move - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Biometric practices have moved around the world through colonial and postcolonial contexts, transnational exchange, and private sector developments. They have become central to a variety of public and private infrastructures. Often, biometric technologies and data are not built from scratch, rather they are reformulated and repurposed to fit new times, places, and contexts. Automated face and fingerprint identification on smartphones, and biometric data in ID cards, are underwritten by similar methods of body measurement developed by 19th and 20th century eugenics, anthropology, statistics, and criminology researchers. States have appropriated biometric databases as digital platforms, which often serve as foundations upon which other infrastructures are organized. Biometric systems have been used, and reused, for purposes ranging from the delivery of government services to policing, from tracking refugees to COVID-19 mitigation efforts. This open track invites submissions that address the movement of biometric practices, and their social consequences. Panelists will explore not only how biometric techniques constitute emerging forms of identity governance, but also how they move across time and place, reorganize existing practices, and produce new kinds of infrastructures. Even in new contexts, biometric systems carry the biases and intentions of prior ones. These systems can fail, and present asymmetrical benefits and harms that reinforce inequalities related to race, gender, class, age, and disability. These systems also shape the lived experiences of citizenship, migration, surveillance, and access to services. This panel welcomes papers that leverage STS concepts and methods to probe the trajectories, implementations, and implications of biometrics on the move.

Participants:

(No)where to Go? Biometric Citizenship and Infrastructures of Financialization *Hanno Moegenburg, University of Konstanz*
Biometric population registers are central to South Africa's redistributive politics today, as they are the base for the state's financial service delivery to millions of its citizens. Celebrated as cutting edge technology for modern governance, I argue, it represents the country's chronology of bodily domination instead: born a tool for British colonial policing and extended during apartheid, the involvement of private economic actors to facilitate today's organisation of the biometric recording contributed to the infrastructure's amalgamation with finance sector's knowledge practices, emerging into a real time system to document and discipline economic behaviour. Herein, the biometric authentication necessary to all essential participations in the country's market economy makes bodily characteristics inevitably complicit in tracking and evaluating customers. At the economic margins, this provoked a run to illegal micro-lenders (Mashonisa), as their arrangements are considered outside the realm of formalised, disciplinary finance. Yet, the relationship

between the informal and the formal credit sector is more complicated and intertwined. By showing how both the re-organisation of debtors' economic strategies as well as informal lenders' business practices by meta-developments of the country's rapid financialization are being mediated through the infrastructuring of biometric information practices, I aim to give example for how digital state-making poses a gateway for new mechanisms of domination within a neoliberal order. Drawing upon classic infrastructure studies, I thereby describe multiple "movements" of biometrics, not only historically or spatial, but also sociologically oscillating between orders of in/formality during the process of infrastructuring.

The Re-Colonial Biometric Marketplace *Yung Au, Oxford Internet Institute*

This paper examines the movement of biometric practices from the West to certain parts of Asia in the form of surveillance-as-a-service subscriptions. In particular, it examines small-to-medium corporations that are not household names but are nevertheless important players in the data industry. Through mapping the flows between these companies and Asian governments, the paper disentangles some of the obscured power relations that surround these firms that regularly fly under the radar. Amrute and Murillo (2020) highlighted the work by postcolonial scholarship in examining the hidden labour of computing worlds which are often grouped under the heading of "outsourcing". This literature has examined how the least lucrative jobs are siphoned overseas to peripheral communities. Building on this work, this paper examines the flip-side: when Western centres of power are the targets of "outsourcing" and when the South becomes reliant on surveillance infrastructures from the West. These under-regulated flows become another way in which colonial dependencies and logics are further entrenched in our systems. There is thus a pressing need to scrutinize the supply chain of today's biometric industry as there are immense agenda-setting powers in corporations that shape the supply and, to some extent, the demand for such services from authorities around the world. Some pertinent questions include: What inequities are created, re-created and reified through the lending of infrastructures and opaque proprietary systems? What does it mean to be reliant on immense caches of data and software that ultimately are designed, calibrated and controlled by the west?

The technopolitics of smart tattoos: from biosecurity to self-monitoring medical art. *Alexis Bedolla*

This presentation explores a relevant discursive transformation regarding smart tattoos in the U.S. context. Through analyzing archives and contemporary documents from the Department of Defense, Microsoft and several universities that are interested in developing these technologies, this presentation argues that smart tattoos are currently undergoing an important semantic shift. A shift that moves away from being identified as devices for detecting chemical, biological and radiological exposure of military personnel, to being identified either as biometric wearable technologies that combine of art and medicine, or as innovative tools for public health surveillance. By comparing the differences in the discursive portrayal of smart tattoos in military documents and big-tech corporations, this presentations explores how the fact that smart tattoos are being made commercially viable, enact different political goals from their original military purposes. Especially, this presentation reflects on how this transformation impacts on the technopolitics of smart tattoos in regards to who collects new forms of biological data? Who owns that data? What novel things can be done with biological data that was not easily accessible before? Who profit from that data? And whose data is being collected?

BodyTeller: Explorations in Narrative Biosensing *Gabrielle Benabdallah, University of Washington; Blair Subbaraman, University of Washington*

Biosensing technologies are increasingly integrated in everyday

consumer level devices such as health tracking watches and mobile phones. How these devices track and inscribe bodies into digital and normative spaces inherits from logics that have historically sought to discipline the body through technical and institutional means. In this history, bodies have been silenced in favor of the measurements they produce. This project seeks to leverage these measurements to let the body tell its own story, through the exploration of expressive modes of biosensing data representation. We present BodyTeller, a biosensing device that creates narratives as data logs. These narratives are first shared between users of the device, making discussion and exchanges necessary steps for the access of one's data. The BodyTeller therefore encourages collective over individual data interpretation and contestable, rather than authoritative, data representation. Drawing from design research and auto-ethnographic encounters with BodyTeller, we outline how the logs work as means of collecting, sharing and making sense of biosensing data over time. We end with two key lessons for biosensing research: para-control (design operating outside techno-determination) and auto-extensions (a method of design inquiry as auto-ethnographic).

Skin-Deep Smiles: Labor, Credit, and Retail in China's Emotion Economy *Shazeda Ahmed, School of Information, University of California- Berkeley; Vidushi Marda, Article 19*

The implementation of emotion recognition technologies in China has foregrounded state efforts at judging individuals' behavior, while raising Chinese citizens' awareness of and pushback against some applications of emotion recognition. Recent work has revealed domestic public criticisms of textual sentiment analysis tools the Chinese government used to track social media opinions on Covid-19 (Wu 2021), along with over two dozen companies' capture of biometric signals such as facial expressions and blood flow, vocal tone, and body movement to assess individuals' "true" emotional states in public security, driving safety, and education contexts (Marda and Ahmed 2021). How do these biometric technologies reconfigure social relations when applied in fields directly related to people's economic livelihoods? This paper draws from Mandarin-language texts on framings of the "emotion economy" (情绪经济, qíngxù jīngjì), investigating how machine learning-driven emotion recognition is applied in loan interviews, retail settings, and two labor contexts: hiring and workplace surveillance. Sources include tech firms' marketing materials and news coverage, and local government funding proposals as well as Chinese academic publications supporting public adoption of these technologies. Building on the literature that argues emotion is expressed differently across cultures, the paper will also bring STS research to bear on how data collection on ethnicity and emotion intersect in these systems. The literature on affect in East Asia (Yang et al 2014), affect in postsocialist Chinese media (Liu 2019), and the affective labor of women in China's tech startup culture (Lindtner 2020) will inform this work's theoretical contributions. References Arcy, Jacquelyn. 2016. "Emotion work: considering gender in digital labor." *Feminist Media Studies*, 16:2, 365-368, doi:10.1080/14680777.2016.1138609. Levy, Karen and Solon Barocas. 2018. "Refractive Surveillance: Monitoring Customers to Manage Workers." *International Journal of Communication* 12(2018), 1166–1188. <https://ijoc.org/index.php/ijoc/article/view/7041>. Lindtner, Silvia. 2020. *Prototype Nation: China and the Contested Promise of Innovation*. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press. Liu, Xiao. 2019. *Information Fantasies: Precarious Mediation in Postsocialist China*. Minneapolis, MN: University of Minnesota Press. Marda, Vidushi and Shazeda Ahmed. 2021. "Emotional Entanglement: China's emotion recognition market and its implications for human rights." Article 19 report. <https://www.article19.org/wp-content/uploads/2021/01/ER-Tech-China-Report.pdf>. Poster, Winifred. 2019. "Sound Bites,

Sentiments, and Accents: Digitizing Communicative Labor in the Era of Global Outsourcing,” in *digitalSTS: A Handbook and Field Guide*, eds David Ribes and Janet Vertesi. Princeton, NJ: Princeton University Press. 240-262. Raghavan, Manish et al. 2019. “Mitigating Bias in Algorithmic Hiring: Evaluating Claims and ACM Conference on Fairness, Accountability, and Transparency (FAT*)." doi:10.2139/ssrn.3408010. Stark, Luke and Karen Levy. 2018. “The surveillant consumer.” *Media, Culture & Society*, 40(8):1202-1220. doi:10.1177/0163443718781985. Stark, Luke, and Jesse Hoey. 2020. “The Ethics of Emotion in AI Systems.” OSF Preprints. doi:10.31219/osf.io/9ad4u. Wu, Angela Xiao. 2021. “Chinese Computing and Computing China as Global Knowledge Production.” *Catalyst: Feminism, Theory, and Technoscience*, 6(2). doi.org/10.28968/cftt.v6i2.34363. Yang, Jie (ed). 2014. *The Political Economy of Affect and Emotion in East Asia*. New York, NY: Routledge.

Session Organizer:

Ranjit Pal Singh, Data & Society Research Institute

Chair:

Michelle Spektor, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

355. Caring Economies II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Second installation of "Caring Economies," including papers on caring economies specific to regimes of valuation in health care, poverty management, and global health.

Participants:

Bio-logics of Poverty: Anthropometrics, Eugenics, and Racism in the Name of Care *Emily Yates-Doerr*

Global institutions such as the World Health Organization and World Bank are busy turning care into a practice of anthropometrics, encouraging policymakers to fight global poverty by collecting data on children's growth. The underlying idea is that much like rings on a tree, bones form an objective linear record -- an archeology -- of the social environment. Children who are well-fed grow taller. Those who are two standard deviations from normal growth reference curves are marked as "stunted," a condition increasingly treated synonymously with poor cognition and ill health. The promise is that these (anthro)metrics will give clear evidence of who is suffering from poverty and where to intervene. This growing global concern for childhood stunting resurfaces one of anthropology's oldest fascinations: the measurement of bodies and heads. Set in Guatemala--widely held to be one of the world's most "stunted countries"-- my paper describes how a range of people (scientists, midwives, mothers) take-up, or reject, the science of anthropometrics. I unpack how global institutions use care to justify the creation of racial difference, their big-data technologies echoing Galton's 20th-century Anthropometric Laboratory and his eugenic theories of fitness and value. I show how "bio-logics of poverty" both produce inequality and hold it in place and ask what other logics of poverty may better achieve poverty's end.

Caring In/ For the Technocracy of Global Health *Steven Black, Georgia State University*

I examine how global health professionals frame the technocratic labor of logistics as care-work, discussing the health equity implications of this framing. I analyze conceptualizations of collaboration, especially the notion of “public-private partnership” and its care-entailments. This is based on my study of public-facing communication of secular global health non-profit organizations (NPOs) in the Atlanta metropolitan region, including interviews with global health leaders, participant-observation at public events, and analysis of Atlanta-based NPOs' websites and YouTube videos. Atlanta, Georgia is a global health hub—one that is centered on connections between

government institutions (the Centers for Disease Control and Prevention [CDC]), universities (eg. Emory University's School of Public Health), and NPOs (eg. the Taskforce for Global Health). Global health professionals associated with these organizations emphasize concepts such as compassion, solidarity, and care even while working primarily with abstractions of public health and valorizing data-driven approaches. I argue that the ethico-moral value of care, discursively linked to notions of partnership and collaboration, plays a key role in the generation of monetary value for NPOs. However, this value production relies on a flattening and erasure of the distinctiveness of contributions from low- and middle-income countries. My analysis provides an explanation of the ways that global health professionals value and mobilize technocracy, while also suggesting that this valuation may end up reinforcing existing inequities in global health.

Microeconomies of Care: Crisis, Responsibility, and Collective Life in the Post-Welfare United States *Talia R Gordon, The University Of Chicago*

This paper theorizes the relationship between “economy” and “care” in the contemporary United States as it is mediated and expressed through particularly American forms of responsibility generated by the post-welfare era's conditions of perpetual crisis. Recent work in anthropology has used the term “post-welfare” to describe how political and economic restructuring reduces social provisions and protections for local subjects, especially for members of already marginalized groups (Elisha 2011, Fennell 2015, Fairbanks 2009, Morgen & Maskovsky 2003, Muehlebach 2012, O'Connor 2000). According to established critiques of neoliberalism, post-welfare subjects learn, through processes of “responsibilization,” to take care of themselves rather than rely on the state (Bulley 2013, Larner 2000, O'Malley 2010, Reid 2012, Rose 1999). However, I argue, as neoliberal capitalism's austerity regimes make individual responsibility and self-sufficiency increasingly untenable modes of life, people are experimenting with more collective ways of being responsible. Drawing on ethnographic research with autoworkers and neighborhood groups in Flint, Michigan — a community perpetually tasked with recovering from crisis — I describe how people orient themselves as responsible subjects through small-scale relations of social intimacy in the absence of a redistributive welfare state. Within these “microeconomies of care,” I suggest, local subjects model shifting notions of responsibility that may reflect broader shifts in the moral/political foundations that give structure and meaning to collective life in the post-welfare U.S. Engaging with conversations in feminist STS and adjacent disciplines about the ethics of care in contemporary societies, this paper interrogates the relations sustaining our intimate worlds.

Relational Histories Of Care For Aging Populations: Valuing Late Life In Poland Across Political-Economic Eras *Jessica C Robbins, Wayne State University*

In contemporary Poland, Universities of the Third Age are the most visible institutional forms of self-care for older adults. These continuing-education institutions that are specifically for retirees often cultivate ideologies of independence through workshops and classes that teach new, and potentially transformative, skills and hobbies. Although Universities of the Third Age may seem to be a model of postsocialist neoliberal ideals of care in late life, two key points belie this assumption. First, the practices through which older Poles strive for independence are themselves fundamentally relational. Second, Universities of the Third Age emerged out of the fields of andragogy, pedagogy, and social work, fields that have regional intellectual roots in the late 19th/early 20th-century presocialist era -- and are based on radically different ideals of relationality and care. This paper draws on ethnographic and historical data to work towards an ethnographically grounded intellectual history of the aging subject in central and eastern Europe. The Polish

case offers an opportunity to think across divergent political-economic eras, in which assumptions about the value of a person to society have shifted. Focusing on the aging subject highlights practices and ideals of care, since economic characterizations of older adults often focus on the axis of independence/dependence. By tracing how the fields of andragogy, pedagogy, and social work have imagined and enacted care for older adults, this paper elucidates connections between economic transformations and constructions of aging subjects, and contributes relational understandings of care in late life that go beyond dichotomies of East/West, socialist/capitalist, and collective/individual.

Session Organizer:

Martha Lincoln, San Francisco State University

Discussant:

Risa Cromer, Purdue University

356. Emergent Orders in the Governance, Institutions and Knowledge Economies of Genome Editing Technologies - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

In the wake of the rapid development of novel genome editing technologies for manipulating DNA, most notably the CRISPR-Cas9 system, a wide variety of actors are vying for influence and access over their governance, development and use. Scientists, biohackers, patients, regulators, bioethicists, disability justice advocates, venture capitalists, biopharma and agriculture firms, among others, are contributing to and contesting the development of institutions for governing these biotechnologies. Key to these dynamics are the discourses, processes and practices through which existing scientific, social, political, economic and ethical orders are disrupted, co-produced, and stabilized to form emergent orders, and how and why some possibilities are opened while others are constrained. This paper session invites research that examines and explores the intertwined development of genome editing technologies and social institutions from diverse perspectives and contexts, and across different applications (e.g. agriculture; health and biomedicine; environmental management and gene drives). What discourses, processes, practices and norms are important for governing these novel biotechnologies? How is increased access to and expanded use of these biotechnologies reconfiguring existing social and institutional orders, and leading to new ones? How can we imagine and enact more democratic forms of engagement with and governance of novel biotechnologies? Overall, we are interested in developing a comparative and critical picture of the emergence of new social orders as the ability to modify DNA becomes commonplace, and in doing so, identify sites where existing inequalities or asymmetries of power are reproduced and can be addressed.

Participants:

Challenges Facing Engagement in Emerging Biotechnology Risk Assessment: Fostering Good Relations in Problematic Contexts *Adam Kokotovich, University of Exeter*

In a world that embraces simple solutions and storylines, why is it important to acknowledge the tension-filled, conflictual, and problematic spaces in which we work? In addition, what intellectual and emotional resources are required to fully comprehend these spaces and skillfully work within them? Ecological risk assessment synthesizes science to inform decision making and is a privileged framework within many national and international governance contexts. While often popularly conceived of as an objective scientific endeavor, there is a long lineage of STS scholarship exploring the normative, political, or values-laden nature of risk assessment. Many have explored how stakeholder engagement can be used to identify, reflect upon, and inform the key value judgments within risk assessment. While engagement offers important incremental improvements to risk assessment, it is often problematically framed as either an unnecessary waste of time or a solution to all problems facing risk assessment. In the context of gene drives and other emerging biotechnologies, these simplistic dichotomous extremes are particularly damaging because they draw attention

away from the important tensions and challenges facing engagement in risk assessment (e.g., concerning: who to include, what to assess, how to define harm, and how to navigate its fundamental limitations). Furthermore, grappling with such tensions is a valuable and necessary step in designing engagement. Through examining the challenges facing engagement in ecological risk assessment for emerging biotechnologies, this presentation will explore what is at stake in how we envision and practice engagement in difficult contexts and what intellectual and emotional skills are supportive.

Is It Time To Move Beyond Risk Assessment? Governing Genome Edited Organisms In India *Shashank Shekhar Tiwari, Canadian Institute for Genomics and Society; Kalina Kamenova, Canadian Institute for Genomics and Society*

The Government of India is planning to introduce new regulations to address the challenges of emerging genome editing technologies and realize their commercial potential in the areas of human health, agriculture, and the environment. The draft document Genome Edited Organisms: Regulatory Framework and Guidelines for Risk Assessment, posted on the Department of Biotechnology (DBT)'s website, has generated a variety of public responses. In this paper, we provide a critical analysis of the proposed guidelines, highlighting the limited scope of regulatory oversight (e.g., focus on risk assessment vs. a Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) framework) and the reliance on ineffective multi-level governance mechanisms for biotechnology (e.g., outdated regulations, legislation, and guidelines) that may not be suitable to address unforeseen environmental and health consequences of gene drives and other radical applications of CRISPR/Cas9 editing system. Drawing on STS approaches to science policy and biotechnology governance, the paper scrutinizes: 1) how the "object of biomedical governance" is constituted in India's policy discourses on gene edited organisms; 2) the limitations of the proposed risk assessment approach; and 3) the need for wider public participation of citizens, citizen groups, policymakers, politicians, and other stakeholders in the development of an ethical framework for gene editing technologies. Finally, we discuss key RRI normative principles that should guide public dialogue on gene editing in India and globally, such as inclusivity, reflexivity, anticipation, and responsiveness.

Resistance relationships in AgBiotech stewardship: evolving good stakeholder relations and knowledge co-production in agricultural pest management *Dalton Robert George, North Carolina State University*

Crop biotechnology has always been tethered to "resistance management", a set of on-farm pest management "best practices" - traditionally developed by expert knowledge - that are designed to maintain the efficacy of herbicide and pesticide resistant crops against the evolutionary capacities of pests. However, networks of farmers often contest these best management practices because they often don't reflect farmers knowledge, values, and priorities related to on-farm pest management. The result is poor management outcomes, because contestation leads to disjointed communication and uncoordinated response to resistance evolution. However, experts in agricultural extension that are embedded in farming communities treat contestation as an opportunity to build a collaborative nexus of shared knowledge, priorities, and values with farmers that come to represent a shared responsibility to bolster best management practices. In addition, farmers that develop trusting relationships with experts who take the time to listen, learn, and embed themselves in the networks of shared responsibility that is responding to the resistance management problem experience better stewardship outcomes. What this creates is a sense of collective responsibility that is tethered to not only the roles of acting as a farmer or extension professional, but roles in the shared community. In this presentation, I will describe empirical research that demonstrates

how knowledge co-production is mediated by the relationships between different actors involved in resistance management. Using a method called qualitative network analysis, I will demonstrate how a comprehensive analysis of network structure, knowledge-exchange interactions, and meaning-making yield insights into how stakeholder relationships respond to the problem of resistance management, and what this means more generally for the stewardship of future agricultural biotechnologies.

Extending Engagement and Engaging Extension in the Land Grant University for Genetic Technologies in Agricultural Systems *S Kathleen Barnhill-Dilling, North Carolina State University*

Decades of STS scholarship has prescribed, described, and contested broader engagement with respect to emerging technologies, particularly in the context of agriculture. The nature of which institutions and actors should facilitate these engagement practices remains an open question, as issues around motivation and conflict of interest persist. Despite their long established place in agricultural knowledge production and transfer, relatively little engagement scholarship has focused on the role of US-based land grant extension systems, whose institutional roles are to engage communities, stakeholders, and wider publics about different parts of the agricultural system including the role of genetic engineering and other biotechnology tools. Drawing on personal situatedness as an engagement scholar/practitioner working in collaboration with extension projects, as well as content analysis of extension media and preliminary interview data, this presentation will interrogate the overlap and incongruencies between STS-derived engagement and land grant extension systems with particular focus on genetic technologies in agricultural systems. More specifically, this presentation will explore how both sets of engagement practices - situated in a US land grant institution -- are (or are not) boundary practices that generate collaborative problem identification and framing, knowledge co-production, and other forms of collaboration, expertise-sharing, and technology transfer.

Engineering Responsibility: Experts, Engagement, and Engineered Gene Drives *Christian H. Ross*

Calls for public engagement around genome editing technologies such as gene drives have been widespread in gene drive governance discourse as a normative imperative to ensure its responsible development and the democratic governance of its potential use. In that discourse, I argue that constructions of public engagement as a marker of what it means to do responsible science to reinforce the authority of scientific expertise by establishing them not only as epistemic authorities but also normative ones. Moreover, the moral imperatives for public engagement also render local and global publics commensurable such that localized instances of engagement can be leveraged to support the use of gene drives elsewhere globally. To do so, I follow the emergence of public engagement across gene drive discourse, with an emphasis on US and related international context, from the first paper on engineered gene drives circa 2014 through the 2016 US National Academies of Science, Engineering and Medicine consensus report on gene drives. I then trace public engagement through its uptake, repackaging, and deployment as a morally-laden, imperative to for the responsible development and democratic governance of gene drives. Analysis of scientific experts as moral stakes-setters provides insight into the ways in which what constitutes public engagement, and thereby, also what constitutes responsible, good governance of gene drives, are constructed in ways that constrains possible avenues of critique for gene drives by counterposing narratives of responsible development of gene drives with those of imagined, irresponsible, and inevitable uses.

Session Organizers:

Dan Santos, Monash University (Australia)

Santiago J Molina, University of California Berkeley

Chair:

Sebastian Zarate, North Carolina State University

357. Legal Technologies: The Need For STS-Analyses - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Data-driven methods such as machine learning and artificial intelligence and their development for and deployment in a wide variety of social and societal contexts are currently experiencing a critical moment of academic, media and political discussion. This applies not least to the realm of law and legal practice: With applications such as forecasting court decisions via machine learning algorithms, automated reading, scanning and creation of legal texts, predictability of legal disputes, participatory tools for democratising legal practice comes the promise of innovation within the legal system. However, this innovation is not always welcomed enthusiastically and requires critical inquiry. An STS perspective is particularly fruitful in this realm when it comes to understanding the implementation dynamics and potential consequences of legal technologies. This open panel invites empirical and theoretical contributions that address the following questions and more: Which actors discuss legal technologies? Who benefits from the envisioned predictive power of machine learning? In what ways are legal practices and epistemologies shaped and reconceptualised by the application of data-driven methods? To what extent can legal technologies contribute to rethinking the relations between the individual and the legal apparatus and thereby contribute to “Good Relations”? Do the conceptual differences between a case-law system and a codified law system play a role in the question of compatibility with Big Data applications? To what extent is the potential of legal technologies overestimated and/or underestimated? How can law be rethought in light of data-driven methods? Is law facing an epistemological conflict between formalist and correlative approaches?

Participants:

Legal Technologies: Epistemic And Normative Implications

Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld; Paola Lopez, University of Vienna

In this paper, we give a systematic definition of legal technologies and present a categorization of different kinds of legal technologies, structured along their supposed epistemic dimension: What kind of knowledge are different technologies in the legal domain supposed to produce? This paper takes an interdisciplinary perspective and therefore combines a technical perspective, which can address the epistemic foundations and thus the epistemic limitations, with a social scientific perspective, which can view legal technologies as a situated and embedded phenomenon. We will critically discuss potential epistemic and practical consequences of artificial intelligence and other data-driven algorithmic methods used in legal practices, and we claim that while certain technologies are being overestimated, others are being underestimated in their epistemic and normative effects. We conclude by looking into democratic and participatory potential of artificial intelligence in the field of law.

Questions of fact and questions of law: algorithmic

classifications and categories as an intersection *Angelika Adensamer, Vienna Centre for Societal Security*

Both civil law and common law jurisdictions traditionally make a difference between “questions of fact” and “questions of law”, where facts are determined by evidence and legal questions are answered by interpretation of the law. This distinction has real consequences, for example in some jurisdictions questions of fact are not considered by higher courts, and therefore have less stages of appeal. The distinction however is not clear cut and can be complicated and even contradictory. When algorithmic legal technologies merge questions of facts with questions of law, for example in cases where legal interpretations are automatically offered after an input of evidential data, this legal distinction becomes a challenge. Most new algorithmic systems rely on

classifications and sorting systems and it is essential to clarify the boundaries of both evidence and norms within them. Classifications and categories have a double function at the intersection of facts and norms. The attribution to a category is often based on facts, whereas the subsequent impact of that attribution is normative. This problem will be exemplified by the case of automated Language Analysis for Determination of Origin (LADO) in asylum procedures as this software potentially conflates questions of facts (correlation of dialect and region) with questions of law (nationality, worthiness of international protection). This contribution will investigate the significance of the legal distinction of questions of fact and questions of law, illustrate some problems that might arise from this and present possible solutions both in terms of technological requirements as well as legal definitions.

Courting Machines: A marriage of convenience? *Petra Gyongyi, University of Oslo*

This paper assesses whether the introduction of new technologies in courts create incentives for judges to uphold the rule of law and enhance the legitimacy of judicial functioning. Or, to the contrary, whether new technologies create a threat or tensions for guaranteeing access to an independent and impartial judge. The paper relies on Mireille Hildebrandt's robust legal technology framework and connects it to theoretical insights of mixing rule of law and new public management mechanisms for enhancing the quality of justice in contemporary societies. Relying on longitudinal comparative case study methodology, the paper shows that new technologies may not only create incentives, such as timeliness, consistency and reducing bias, but also tensions. More precisely, the autonomy of individual judges within the organisation and independent decision-making are such areas of tension. Robust court technologies rely on a constant feedback-loop from judges and judicial associations. The paper focuses on three case studies: the European Court of Human Rights as a transnational leader of adopting data-driven technology; experiences in Central and Eastern Europe (i.e. Romania and Bulgaria), adopting automated case allocation methods since 2005 and with digitisation and full publication of case law; and historical examples of introducing new technologies. The paper relies on content analysis of legislative and policy documents, as well as archival documents. Overall, this analysis broadens the theoretical and empirical framework for studying the digitisation of courts with considerations regarding the incorporation of new court technologies in a transnational or fragile rule of law framework.

Session Organizers:

Simon Egbert, University of Bielefeld

Paola Lopez, University of Vienna

Chair:

Nikolaus Poehhacker, University of Graz

358. Quantum Technologies as Technological Promise: Toward an Uncertain Future - II: Responsible Futures of Quantum Technologies

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Participants:

Conditional Futures of Quantum Technologies *Zeki Can Seskir, Middle East Technical University*

Quantum technologies is an emerging field of technologies with major implications expected for both scientific progress and societal impact. Foreseeing a path forward for any new and emerging sciences and technologies (NEST) is a challenging but essential topic for future studies, policymaking, and technology assessment. In this study, considering technology not just as a collection of technical feats but also as a field of emergence for socioeconomic, cultural, and political relations, I aim to ask the following questions; (i) How are quantum technologies

imagined, envisioned, and aimed to be realized in our current techno-societies? (ii) What are the possible path dependencies for future scenarios for the development of these technologies? A roadmap for this study will be presented here including the literature review, previous work, gathered data, and some preliminary analysis. Several concepts of inquiry will also be introduced such as quantum literacy, quantum awareness, quantum divide, quantum race, and quantum apocalypse. The emergence of these new 'quantum' futures, and how to approach this phenomenon through the lenses of STS research will be opened up for discussion.

Schroedinger's revolution: Overhyped but underestimated? *Philip Inglesant, University of Oxford, Department of Computer Science; Marina Jirotko, University of Oxford, Department of Computer Science; Carolyn Ten Holter, Department of Computer Science, University of Oxford; Robin Williams, The University of Edinburgh*

"Quantum 2.0" technologies - quantum communications, quantum measurement, quantum imaging, and quantum computing - are linked in the imagination only by their reliance on insights of quantum physics. A sociotechnical analysis of the promise of quantum technologies and their revolutions therefore requires a sharper focus. This paper focuses on quantum computing from our work embedded in the UK's Networked Quantum Information Technologies Hub from 2014 to 2019. Quantum computing is a contested space, not only in competing implementations of which one may emerge as the "winner", but in the ontological question of what quantum computing is: "universal error-corrected quantum computing", "Noisy Intermediate-Scale" or "possibly quantum, possibly useful" specialised implementations such as D-Wave. The physical realisation of quantum computing technologies will mutually shape the institutions in which they are embedded. Incumbent companies are competing for "supremacy" and to offer quantum computing services at scale; meanwhile, insurgent SMEs provide specialised expertise in quantum algorithms and applications including machine learning, materials, and logistics. However, as with many emerging technologies, quantum computing is surrounded by hype which obscures rather than illuminates its capabilities and the structural transformations which it might engender. Whether quantum computing opens "a new computer technology era more powerful than anything that preceded it" (Khan 2021), or is merely useful for certain hard computing problems, the democratisation and development of these technologies in the public interest depends not only of the affordances of the technology but more fundamentally on the control, form, structure, and ownership of these institutions.

Towards Quantum Technology Assessment *Christopher Coenen, KIT-ITAS; Armin Grunwald*

Some time ago, we argued for a differentiated stakeholder dialogue model in which the various application areas of quantum technology are largely treated separately, with a view to the different degrees of urgency in terms of societal consultation needs and by privileging representatives of civil society organisations that are specifically interested and competent in these application areas (Coenen & Grunwald 2017). In terms of public dialogue and other public communication activities that are primarily intended to educate or promote societal reflection on the field as a whole and its long-term perspectives, we recommended choosing a broad thematic framework that supports a better understanding of the current state of the art in the field and its short-term perspectives, while at the same time not excluding longer-term and imaginative perspectives, especially by including art-science interactions. Meanwhile, funding for quantum science and technology has increased dramatically, including public funding. We now argue that much greater and more diverse efforts are needed regarding the societal aspects of this emerging field of technoscience. In our paper, we

will provide some reflections from a technology assessment (TA) perspective and present the first results of an ongoing scoping study we are currently conducting on the field of quantum technology, expectations and visions for the future in this field, and societal aspects, focusing on the EU and Germany. The TA perspective will be contextualised in reflections on the future of quantum STS more broadly and include discussions on ethical issues.

Session Organizer:

Zeki Can Seskir, Middle East Technical University

Discussant:

Susannah Glickman, Columbia University

359. Re-thinking And Experimenting With Participatory Research Practices And Design Through The Speculative And Ontological Turn - III: Environmental / Multispecies

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Growing Codesign: Developing Plant-human Participatory Practice *Raune Frankjaer; Lone Koefoed Hansen, Aarhus University*

Despite growing environmental concerns, we know little about how to include the environment into design processes. We tend to focus on the obstacles afforded by the non-verbal nature of natural entities to the design process, which are often perceived as being unsurmountable. However, Codesign has an array of methods aimed at designing with groups unable to articulate their needs. In addition, new sensing technology and corresponding research from plant science allows us to read basic plant-signals, enabling us to gauge plant responses. In this paper we present first findings from Growing Codesign, a project that combines participatory design practice with insights from plant science and bioelectric sensing technology to develop a set of collaborative human-plant design methods. Positioning plants as participatory entities may seem peculiar as participation is commonly understood as describing a distinct and conscious act. However, in Codesign several distinctions have been made with regard to kinds of participants and types of participation. Participants are not merely explicit users but includes stakeholders, i.e. those who do not use a design but nevertheless are affected by it. Moreover, participation does not necessitate direct action but may be representative or even imagined. The project employs an experimental approach, building on a theoretical foundation from design research, art and Codesign, set within a larger posthumanist and post-anthropocentric framework.

Living Brood Lac Bank: A case-study for multi-sited ethnography for navigating multiple epistemologies *Vinisha Singh Basnet, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign*

Engaging with multiple epistemologies (ways of knowing), also termed as 'epistemological pluralism' is well theorized by scholars working at the cusp of disciplines. However, we need more case-studies to provide different ways of incorporating 'epistemological pluralism' in practice-based research. This paper attempts to provide one such example of conducting an action-research that incorporates different ways of seeing and understanding the relationship between the host plants and an economically important insect species, *Kerria lacca*. Rearing *Kerria lacca* is one of the main livelihood source of many indigenous, forest-dependent-communities in central India, and its diminishing population from the nearby forest has been a serious threat to that source of livelihood. Drawing from two-and-a-half years of multi-sited ethnography and participatory action research my work inquires factors attributing to the vanishing insect population. My work extensively engages with the scientists, government & non-governmental actors, and the indigenous communities. Therefore, calls for navigating through

different ways of knowing plant-insect relationship for sustainable rearing process. As a result of engaging with multiple epistemologies I propose an action plan, called Living Brood Lac Bank (an in-situ germplasm repository of *Kerria lacca*) to strengthen the livelihood source of the local communities. It concludes highlighting key challenges of bringing science(s), societies and natural world together.

The Food Computer and the Effable Plant *Danial Qaurooni, 325 E. 10th St.*

My presentation is based on dissertation fieldwork on the plant-computer interface in the case of the Food Computer, a device designed at the MIT Media Lab (2015-2020). One distinguishing feature of the Food Computer was that it ran Climate Recipes, algorithmic control structures that would optimize plant growth by regulating climate components (e.g. light, temperature, nutrients) to produce desirable expressions of flavor, nutrient density, or size in the plant. In my presentation, I first argue that Climate Recipes are solipsist control structures that ignore the multiple, diverging perspectives dwelling in the Food Computer's growth chamber, including the plant's. My critique of solipsism then poses the question of adopting perspective. Avoiding epistemological framings à la What is it like to be a plant? (Nagel 1974), I advocate for a relational approach to this question (Strathern 1988, de Castro 2013). Perspectives are not private chambers of lived experience but public points of view that can be adopted by attending to the relations that constitute them (Strathern 1988), relations that are primarily neither physiological nor mental (e.g. Kohn 2013) but dispositional. The plant as a bundle of everyday dispositions – e.g. "tropisms," feeding and growing habits, and kinship relations – might be more familiar to the gardener than the technologist, the botanist, or the philosopher. Finally, when it comes to the plant-computer interface, the interspecies barrier might not be whether/how plants can think but how concepts like intelligence can be reconstituted to betray their genealogy in a gesture of openness towards the plant's perspective.

When Being isn't Enough: Doing, Making and Becoming as a Design Move *Ann Light, University of Sussex*

As Danholt and Wilkie argue (4S call, 2021): the ontological turn should not be merely the replacing of Western ontology with sociomaterial interwovenness, but rather a move to plurality and even to "overthrow ontology". Yet, accepting plural worlds, while sensitive to difference and the need for socio-ecological justice, offers the spectre of situating humanity in a hall of ontological mirrors, where everything is fragmented. In this philosophical scenario, rapid material progress to un-liveability is hastened by the impossibility of joint action to respect the shared planet. Alternatively, we must find a meta-story, a narrative that allows for the turn itself and for motion distinct from the totalising stories of western modernity and progress. To do so requires us to consider temporal dimensions, not only of speculation, but of worlding as an enactment and the performance of transformations. Without this appeal to collective doing, making and becoming (however diverse), all designing, participatory practice and other potentially restorative engagements that attempt to embrace plural ontologies will be subtly co-opted by fatal neo-liberal processes that already fragment through hierarchies of difference. I once explored the détente of making political tools together as a form of strategic essentialism (2019). Now I am asking how acknowledging ontological tensions and cutting plurality with other heterodoxies can enable fellow-travelling. Light, A. (2019) *The Détente Model of Managing Divergent Values in the Maker Sphere*, in (eds) Jeremy Hunzinger and Andrew Schrock *Making Our World: the Hacker and Maker Movements in Context*, New York: Peter Lang

Equivocal encounters in more-than-human prototyping *Pablo Ignacio Hermansen, Pontificia Universidad Católica de*

Chile; *Martin Tironi*

Faced with the ecological collapse and the socio-natural catastrophes that mark the advent of the Anthropocene, in recent decades the interest in questioning the notion of coexistence beyond human limits has been highlighted. The spread of the coronavirus on the planet has only radicalized the concern on the relationships we establish with non-human entities in more-than-human environments. But to coexist sustainably with other ontologies, human beings need to overcome the self-perception of being exceptional and, at the same time, point of reference for all the other-than-human entities that inhabit the planet. For designers, planners, and other experts, this implies at least slowing down the will to impose anthroponormative scripts through unilaterally designed environments. In what follows, we will portray a more-than-human equivocal experience, occurred during the prototyping of an electronic sound instrument we designed for Judy & Gombe, a chimpanzee couple living at the National Zoo of Chile. After observing the destructive consequences of one Judy & Gombe' intrusion into the structure of the instrument, we interpreted their action as the failure of our coexistence. But the review of the video recording of this imponderable situation, refuted our initial anthropocentric interpretation. Our experience not only shows that it is problematic to project human qualities and defects to interpret the behavior of other species, but also that we have a long way to go to understand and sustainably coexist within more-than-human environments

Session Organizer:

Peter Danholt, Aarhus University

360. A Conversation on Drones, Robots and Mechanization of Politics: Unmanning and Research In-Progress

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

This panel examines contemporary scholarship devoted to drones, robots and algorithmic war, expanding on Katherine Chandler's *Unmanning: How Humans, Machines and Media Perform Drone Warfare* (2020). It puts the book in conversation with four scholars who transform current research on drone warfare by foregrounding science and technology studies, critical race theory, gender studies and media studies. Unmanning considers failed experiments by the United States military to unman aircraft in the twentieth century. It analyzes how the drone's human, machine and media parts are entangled with gender, race and nation. Through unmanning, political actions are disavowed as technological advances, while drone failures underline the limits of seeing from above. In response, Iván Chaar López will expand on the interrelation between the drone and nation, drawing from his monograph-in-progress *The Cybernetic Border: Drones, Technology and Intrusion*. J.D. Schnepf will discuss her work-in-progress, *Drones and Domesticity: Women's Work and the Maintenance of U.S. Imperial Culture*, elaborating on themes of gender and US imperialism. Margaret Rhee will draw on her manuscript, *How We Became Human: Race, Robots and the Asian American Body*, to underline themes of race, technology and embodiment. Allen Feldman, author of "Of the Pointless View" in *War and Algorithm* (2019), will consider the visual culture of drone warfare.

Presenters:

Iván Chaar López, The University of Texas at Austin

J.D. Schnepf, University of Groningen

Margaret Rhee, University at Buffalo

Allen Feldman, New York University

Katherine Chandler

Session Organizer:

Katherine Chandler

Chair:

Kris Fallon, University of California, Davis

361. Un/Making a Difference 4: bodies, embodiment, feminist/crip technoscience design & practice

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Participants:

Disabled and Disobedient: Using Smart Medical Devices *Laura Forlano*, *Illinois Institute of Technology*

This paper, based on an in-progress book manuscript, considers mundane everyday forms of resistance in the lives of disabled people that use "smart" medical devices with a focus on diabetics that use "automated" insulin pumps, which have become commercially available in the United States and around the world in the past four years. Specifically, based on a decade of autoethnographic observation and lived experience (Forlano 2017), which has been framed through feminist (Haraway 1988) and crip (Kafer 2013) technoscience, this paper considers the ways in which these "users" are disobedient – of doctors, insurers, diabetes educators, technology support professionals as well as capitalist temporalities and logics—thereby introducing deliberate friction into the systems for a variety of reasons including cost savings, autonomy, self-knowledge and self-preservation. In contrast to an industry that is obsessed with behavior change and persuasive design, nudging "users" to abide by their rules, disabled people use social media to share their own hacks, tips and fixes to the problems introduced by the so-called "technology solution". For example, these everyday forms of resistance include: how often medical supplies are ordered and used, when to turn off automated functions rather than suffer their consequences, sharing extra medical supplies through mutual aid as well as advocacy around the cost of essential medications. How might human-machine relations differ if, rather than controlling the "user", disobedience was used as a metaphor to frame more generous relations between humans and machines? Forlano, L. (2017) 'Data Rituals in Intimate Infrastructures: Crip Time and the Disabled Cyborg Body as an Epistemic Site of Feminist Science', *Catalyst: Feminism, Theory, Technoscience*, 3(2). Haraway, D. (1988) 'Situated knowledges: The science question in feminism and the privilege of partial perspective', *Feminist studies*, 14(3): 575-99. Kafer, A. (2013) *Feminist, queer, crip*: Indiana University Press.

Diabetes Identity: A Mechanism of Social Change *Heather Rose Walker*, *University of Utah Health*; *Michelle Litchman*, *Professor*; *University of Utah*

Historically, diabetes identity has been examined at the individual level as it relates to clinical outcomes and self-management practices. Yet, identity is not experienced as an individually isolated phenomenon. The purpose of this study is twofold: (a) examine the social meaning of diabetes identity and (b) formulate a theoretical model of diabetes identity through a sociopolitical lens. Adults living with diabetes engaged in a diabetes online community (N = 20) participated in a 60-minute semi-structured interview focused on social diabetes experiences and diabetes identity. Seven themes emerged related to illness, individuation, and culture, resulting in a novel theoretical model of diabetes identity: willingness to identify, tales of the un-sick, legends of the responsible, a tradition of change-making, sense of sameness, mystification of difference, and diabetes as a unifying social category. Our study extends previous literature focused on self-management practices and compliance, resulting in a theoretical model of diabetes identity centered around social change. Shifting the framing of identity in diabetes to center on power and politics prompted several critical questions pertinent to STS which we explore in this presentation: How has medical science assembled itself as the arbiter of diabetic identity and its integration? How can experiential and embodied diabetic knowledges infiltrate medicalized conceptions of diabetic identity? And, how does the public evolution of diabetes identity across social medias create a watershed moment for the public to reconsider what it means to have diabetes today?

Fashion Hacking as Crip Technoscience: The Desire Lines

Generated by Disabled, Deaf and Mad Wearers *Ben Barry, Ryerson University*

New innovations in adaptive clothing and wearable technologies aim to provide improved access and aesthetics to disability-identified wearers. However, the commercial motives of most fashion brands have restricted access for many disability-identified people because of the financial barriers that they face due to ableism and other interlocking systems of oppression. Grounded in Crip Technoscience (Hamraie and Fritsch 2019), this paper explores alternatives to profit-driven adaptive fashion that enable Crip communities to affirm and assert their embodied selves in an ableist and sanist world. I draw on research from the Crippling Masculinity project that engaged 70 disability, d/Deaf and Mad-identified people of diverse races, gender identities and other subject positions. Participants first took part in wardrobe interviews to explore their relationships with clothing, and then engaged in fashion hacking workshops to deconstruct and reconstruct existing garments to fit their bodies and express their identities. My analysis presents the everyday material and embodied strategies enacted by participants to transform clothing originally designed according to the tenants of compulsory able-bodiedness for their disability, d/Deaf and Mad minds-bodies. I then present the preliminary outcomes of the fashion hacking workshops to reveal how interdependence, skill-sharing and community mobilization can extend individual fashion strategies to resist systems of power. By centering the imaginative brilliance of Crip community to create fashion that fosters their embodied and collective belonging, the paper highlights the ‘desire lines’ of fashion design technologies that disrupt the logics and consequences of capitalism, compulsory able-bodiedness and other systems of power.

Care, Cure and Contradiction: Investigating Disabled Clothing Inventions as Objects of Resistance *Ellen Fowles, Goldsmiths, University of London; Kat Jungnickel, Goldsmiths, University of London*

This session uses words, images and material artefacts to discuss tensions between interdependence and personal agency in clothing invented for, with, and by, disabled people. It involves wearer-centred research, which builds upon Hendren and Lynch’s (2016) ‘user-initiated design’ to engage with disabled people as experts. We analyse adaptive clothing inventions in the ERC funded Politics of Patents (POP) project to explore perceptions of disability, identity and authority. Examining which bodies are seen as ‘able’, ‘productive’ and ‘normal’ reveals who has been included and excluded from these categories; the disabled ‘misfits’ who make up the world’s largest minority (Garland-Thomson 2011). Historic clothing patents can also reveal complicated socio-political frictions. We explore patent data in three interweaving themes of Care, Cure and Contradiction. Care refers to inventions that embrace multiplicity through altering the built environment to fit the spectrum of humanity, including universal design influenced by social model of disability. Cure focuses on clothing inventions that aim to fix or eliminate disability by manipulating the body, such as design for rehabilitation. Contradiction examines clothing designs that appear to stray from the norm and provide material evidence of inventors actively rejecting the socio-political standardization of bodies. These inventors refuse to accept impairment as a problem in need of fixing, and instead propose alternative accessible futures. Guided by Hamraie and Fritsch’s (2019) Crip Technoscience Manifesto, we ask how and in what ways inventors resist and subvert ableist assumptions through everyday ‘practices of critique, alteration, and reinvention of our material-discursive world’.

Unmaking and Deviations: How feminisms are informed and enacted in co-design practice *Hannah Korsmeyer*

This article discusses how co-design practice can engage with conditions that constrain and limit decision-making processes

and collaborative visions for more just futures. The research first explores power and co-design practice from an intersectional feminist lens. It then discusses how practitioner commitments to social justice manifest in subtle efforts to “radicalise the mundane” within co-design practice. Many practitioners believe that the right co-design materials and collaborative context can create openings for more critical exploration and collective questioning of established norms. However, this work responds to a notable gap in the literature by interrogating how an individual practitioner’s perspective and theoretical understanding of feminisms becomes enacted or manifested within co-design materials and applied projects. Rather than exploring what feminist co-design practitioners are doing (in terms of project outcomes), this work seeks a better understanding of how this abductive practice is negotiated. The article shares a collection of first-person practice narratives of granular “feminist tendencies” (Ahmed 2017) that have become manifested in co-design materials. It explores how feminist materials and supporting mundane design decisions came about, as well as illustrating how engagement with the co-design process itself contributes back to an evolving personal feminist perspective at the scale of an individual practitioner. Through sharing granular practice narratives and personal accounts of shifting perspectives, this article seeks to establish a humble basis for better evidencing the transformative potential of co-design to help explore alternative possibilities. Inspired by the words of feminist scholar Sara Ahmed, these stories from practice seek to both answer and provoke the question: in co-designing more feminist futures, how are we unmaking how hard it is to deviate from what we have come to expect?

Session Organizer:

Kat Jungnickel, Goldsmiths, University of London

Chairs:

Åsa Ståhl, Department of Design, Linnaeus University
kristina lindström, Malmö University

362. Art, Science and Technology Studies - III: Infrastructure and Institutions of Art and Science

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Chairs: Kathryn de Ridder-Vignone and Steph Jordan

Participants:

The Collaborative Art–Science Project (and Its Discontents)
Silvia Casini, University of Aberdeen

Scholars and practitioners willing to venture in art–science collaboration should start reading those pages that never get listed in any institutional “art–science” literature. A good example is *Atlante Occidentale* (Western Atlas), the book conceived by Daniele Del Giudice during a residency at CERN in 1984 and documented by fieldwork notes. An accidental collision between two small airplanes kicks off the encounter and then friendship between the protagonists, the young CERN physicist Pietro Brahe and the old writer Ira Epstein. The two characters have a common obsession: describing the world. Pietro tries it out by exploring subatomic particles inside a huge underground ring dug under the Jura mountains; Ira abdicates his profession as an analytic weaver of stories. Both are seeking to create new tools (machines) for understanding reality—Pietro a particle collider, Ira the written word. My paper is grounded in work I conducted on the epistemological, aesthetic, and historical role played by data-visualization practices across contemporary biomedicine, neuroscience, and the arts (Casini 2021). I argue that another scale and syntax for art–science projects can emerge from the less structured, more tentative, slower-paced grassroots approaches to setting up collaborative projects. Borrowing concepts such as “mangle of practice” (Pickering) or, more recently, “multiple ontologies” (Mol), “vibrant matter” (Bennett) and “agential realism” (Barad), I show how paying attention to

aesthetics and bricolage in science practice would help cultivate a community of science “amateurs” and “connoisseurs” for whom matters of concern are as important as matters of fact.

Academic artists’ engagement and commercialisation *Joaquín M. Azagra-Caro; Carlos Benito-Amat, INGENIO (CSIC-Universitat Politècnica de València); Ester Planells-Alexandre, INGENIO (CSIC-Universitat Politècnica de València)*

Academic artists are researchers who create artistic work. They form part of the cultural life of cities and contribute to welfare not only through research but also through art. They may commercialise their art or use it to engage in scientific knowledge diffusion. The resources needed to develop and diffuse art in addition to conducting research, may exclude women researchers and contribute to their marginalisation in science, and may be incompatible with a career focused on science quality or an organisational logic based on scientific prestige. We study the responses to a survey of some 7,000 Spanish academics and compare university researchers to other researchers. More than half of the researchers surveyed create artistic work; however, whereas engagement is the norm rather than the exception, commercialisation is rare. Being a woman researcher, working in a university and producing good quality science run counter with being an artist. More younger researchers are artists, but commercial rather than engaged. The detrimental effect of science quality on being a commercial or engaged artist turns positive after a certain threshold, which suggests polarisation among academic artists. Among commercial artists, this polarisation seems to apply specifically to university researchers. We discuss the implications for the valorisation of art across interaction channels and in research evaluations.

Art-science: An Old Practice, A New Discipline. *Autumn Brown, Science Gallery Dublin*

Informal spaces in which art and science come together have proven to be grounds for imagination, and the prototyping of ideas where, a different form of inquiry and experimentation are possible. Evidence suggests that these transdisciplinary approaches open up new and more inclusive avenues of dialogue around complex scientific, technological, and societal issues. Spaces featuring the blended work of artists, scientists, and technologists allow broad audiences to examine representations and performances of the future. This paper examines the historical role of art-science in reflecting patterns of the scientific and technological imagination as well as impacts on the current and future culture of scientific research from subaltern voices including rural and migrant communities in Ireland. In places like Science Gallery Dublin where visions of the future can be shared, constructed, and contested, what kind of impacts do we see on the identity, learning, and attitudes of our participants and institutional collaborators? Where do their values meet and diverge? Preliminary results are shared from a research project examining the effects of art-science engagement on institutional and community participants across Ireland. The development, implementation, and impacts of the project including its efficacy in supporting participants across knowledge producing communities will be shared. When disciplinary borders are crossed or dismantled, are we creating opportunities for knowledge to be made and valued in new and more equitable ways?

ArtSciLab: Experimental Publishing and Knowledge Production in Collaborative Transdisciplinary Practices *Alex Garcia Topete, Nowadays Orange Labs; Cassini Nazir, University of North Texas; Roger Malina, Professor; Charles Lilly, PhD Candidate*

Merging art, science, and technology demands experimentation at the individual and collective level interconnecting not only

different experts but also different stakeholders and sectors of society. With that end goal, collaborative work involves a transdisciplinary intelligence that allows for the inception and execution of hybrid projects and knowledge exchange across domains. In this chapter, the authors discuss ARTECA, a new experimental publishing platform built by MIT Press, Leonardo/ISAST, and the ArtSciLab, a transdisciplinary group of the University of Texas at Dallas. Both the platform and the lab are evidence that the production of knowledge in arts, science, and technology, and the success of transdisciplinary collaborations are correlated to experiments in publishing that allow for the engagement of diverse publics and the manifestation of research in a multiplicity of forms and outcomes.

Session Organizer:

Kathryn de Ridder-Vignone, South Carolina Governor's School for Science & Mathematics

Chair:

Stephanie Beth Jordan, Michigan State University

363. Academic Automation: Machine (un)learning /Artificial (non)intelligence - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Over the last 70 years, computational and networked media have become deeply integrated with higher education and have slowly adopted and integrated various technologies. The newest generation of technologies engaging higher education centers around what is popularly called artificial intelligence, otherwise known as machine learning. Machine learning creates models that, in part self-design solutions that may include interaction, prediction, and other simulatable aspects. This paper argues that significant elements of human interaction and democratic education are demonstrably lost when elements of the educational milieu are automated. While there are plenty of automatic grading examples, artificial teaching assistants and robotic instructors already occurring in specific contexts, and those are seemingly claimed successfully in those contexts. Also, one has to admit that if we are to treat people as humans, we cannot give humans jobs that could be performed entirely by an automaton because otherwise, we would just be treating the humans as if they were automatons. That said, this paper uses examples from the new crop of AI/Machine learning companies and the related discourse to argue that what they teach, communicationaly, isn't necessarily what should be taught if we are to have a democratic society. The discourse tends to ignore democratic issues in favor of matters of labor and efficiency. However, in the research, teaching, and service environments of higher education, while labour issues are prevalent, they pale to governance problems, human communicational literacies, and strategic wisdom core to democratic learning. Following Ivan Illich's unschooling, this paper uses that evidence and argument to show that as human educational technology progresses, it envelops the ideas of the institutions it exists within. I argue that this will parallel the unlearning and unintelligent AI systems as they have to 'learn' and be 'taught' from increasingly less capably educated populations, creating a spiral to the bottom. Thus the parallel interaction between decreased human interaction from a weakened democratic education combined with the increase in machine-assisted learning will undermine the machines' capacity to learn, which will then feedback into the system, weakening it further. This can be resisted both by choosing better technologies and changing the discourse to center on the priorities of higher education, which should be the creating a free society with educated citizens who can communicate effectively in pursuit of the good life (or some variation thereof). With that sort of direction, the ai/learning machines can be trained specifically to those or similar human goods.

Participants:

Artificial Un/intelligence in the Higher Education Classroom
Jeremy Hunsinger, Wilfrid Laurier University

The newest generation of technologies engaging higher education centers around what is popularly called artificial intelligence, otherwise known as machine learning. Machine learning creates

models that, in part self-design solutions that may include interaction, prediction, and other simulatable aspects. This paper argues that significant elements of human interaction and democratic education are demonstrably lost when aspects of the educational milieu are automated. While there are plenty of examples of automatic grading, artificial teaching assistants and robotic instructors already occurring in specific contexts, and those are seemingly claimed successfully in those contexts. Also, one has to admit that if we are to treat people as humans, we cannot give humans jobs that could be performed entirely by an automaton because otherwise, we would just be treating the humans as if they were automatons. That said, this paper uses examples from the new crop of AI/Machine learning companies and the related discourse to argue that what they teach, communicationally, isn't necessarily what should be taught if we are to have a democratic society. The discourse tends to ignore democratic issues in favor of matters of labor and efficiency. However, in the research, teaching, and service environments of higher education, while labour issues are prevalent, they pale to governance problems, human communicational literacies, strategic wisdom that are core to democratic learning. Following Ivan Illich's unschooling, this paper uses that evidence and argument to show that as human educational technology progresses, it envelops the ideas of the institutions it exists within. I argue that this will parallel the unlearning and unintelligent AI systems as they have to 'learn' and be 'taught' from increasingly less capably educated populations, creating a spiral to the bottom. Thus the parallel interaction between decreased human interaction from a weakened democratic education combined with the increase in machine-assisted learning will undermine the machines' capacity to learn, which will then feedback into the system, weakening it further. This can be resisted both by choosing better technologies and changing the discourse to center on the priorities of higher education, which should be the creating a free society with educated citizens who can communicate effectively in pursuit of the good life (or some variation thereof). With that sort of direction, the ai/learning machines can be trained specifically to those or similar human goods.

The Labor Of EdTech: Automation And Integration In Remote Learning Tools *Mario Khreiché, New York University*

The Covid-19 pandemic has served as a catalyst in the education technology (EdTech) sector. In particular, the video software provider Zoom has established itself firmly in the information infrastructure of higher education. In the same space, albeit somewhat less visible, remote learning tools such as Class, Engageli, and Panopto seek to replace, enhance, or integrate with Zoom. Billed as automated solutions for teaching challenges by technologists and administrators, these tools reorganize pedagogic work, value accumulation, and data access. Digital learning tools introduce logics from so-called learning management systems (LMS) into the remote classroom and thus automate not only educational infrastructures, but also lived experiences of teaching and learning. In the case of Panopto, for instance, significant value is added retroactively by assigning recorded lectures to folders and creating searchable text archives using machine learning techniques. As is often the case with logistical matters of this type, students and teachers are typically not adequately involved or represented in decision-making processes, which has implications for data access, ownership, and power relations in the university. Employing a technographic framework, the paper draws from Ben Williamsom's work on datafication and APIs and Bernard Stiegler's idea of grammatization to develop a critical perspective on remote learning tools.

Understanding Weapons of Zoom Disruption: Or How I Learned to Stop Worrying and Love the Zoom Bomb *Arund Jacob, University of Toronto*

Zoom Video Communications has been one of those techno-

solution providers that have answered the neoliberal clarion call to never let a serious crisis go to waste. As academia switched to emergency response teaching/online instruction, we experienced what would the internet look like without commercial content moderators working at breakneck speed to clear the smut and filth that accumulates on the internet. Zoombombing was the Virilioian accident and form of abuse that was the emerging social phenomenon out of Zoom. Meeting links would be posted on Reddit, Twitter, Discord, and various other social media sites to assemble a hoard of users to swarm/rush into the meeting and crash them. In other cases, graphic images, racist, sexist slurs and various other offensive content are broadcast to the Zoom classroom meetings, especially targeting female and BIPOC instructors. These disruptions are then paraded around on platforms such as TikTok with much gleeful enthusiasm as a form of recreational nastiness, the kind of virulent media that gets traction on social media. The academic institution, in its attempts to maintain the facade that everything is tickety-boo, fails to recognize how the most vulnerable members of their community are affected by the forced migration of tasks to online venues. The toxicity of the internet does not seem to titrate down even during a global pandemic. The content moderators not being around to wipe the surfaces down and sanitize these surfaces becomes clearly evident in this potent example.

Wikipedia as Open Pedagogy *Zachary J McDowell, University of Illinois at Chicago*

Recent and ongoing research into utilizing Wikipedia in the classroom suggests a variety of benefits from engaging with the world's largest open knowledge repository. This paper begins from a finding concerning the value students and instructors place on information literacy skills and Wikipedia assignments (McDowell and Stewart, 2017). In addition to this finding, responses to both surveys and focus groups suggest that students directly engaged concepts outlined in the Association of College and Research Libraries (ACRL) Framework for Information Literacy in Higher Education, particularly when engaging understandings of systemic biases, construction of information, and value of information. Putting these findings in conversation with issues of inclusion and marginalization yields significant insights into the connections between critical information literacy, open educational resource (OER), and social justice concerns. Wikipedia functions as the world's largest OER, built by volunteers that collaborate on both the production of knowledge as well as the production of policies and guidelines. This paper will continue to unpack the aforementioned research and help frame these in through the understandings of Wikipedia as a collaborative space of knowledge production in conjunction with ACRL's information literacy standards and framework, illustrating how core concepts within Wikipedia as an OER can be framed into open educational practices (OEPs) to assist in instilling these teachings, and better framing Wikipedia's OEP's as social justice pedagogy.

Session Organizer:

Jeremy Hunsinger, Wilfrid Laurier University

364. Can it scale? Big Tech, entrepreneurship, the scalability zeitgeist, and the role of STS - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Participants:

Scales of Innovation and Flipping Startups to Big Tech *Jacob Hellman*

Entities which appear to exist at different scales may, when approached through process and relation, collapse into one another. This paper considers how big tech grows through mergers and acquisitions, and the recent regulatory scrutiny these have received. Competition and innovation are generally presented as threatened by these dominant firms' acquisitions of

smaller competitors. What is rarely recognized is that big tech's M&A owes not only to its own appetite; many technology startups want to get acquired. Even critical discussions of monopoly tend to reify big tech and startups as independent units of analysis. This obscures the fact that big tech has not grown independently of all the entrepreneurs who make themselves acquisition targets, and the active role of venture capital in scaling up these nascent companies until suitably sized for acquisition. This paper draws on interviews with entrepreneurs and corporate consultants. It contributes to studies of big tech in relation to markets and innovation, suggesting that their market power is culturally distributed across other entities, networks, interests. Analysis of these different scales helps explain the contradiction that Birch (2017) and others have pointed out in contemporary political economy between the dominance of corporate monopoly and the ideological affirmation of free markets. Birch, Kean. 2017. A Research Agenda for Neoliberalism.

Scaling data: From warehouses to lakes, from mining to learning *Christophe Prieur, Telecom Paris*

During the past decade, data have become big. At least that's how they have been called. However they may already have been big in the 1990's, when engineers designed technical infrastructures (and concepts, but Starr, 1999, tells us infrastructures embed concepts) such as so-called data marts, data warehouses and OLAP cubes to collect, store and analyse them. This sophisticated set of tools were used to domesticate the complexity and size of data, and framed a dominant field in information technology... before getting outdated along the next decade (2000's) by new tools, concepts, infrastructures. The new generation of tools were built upon an opposite vision: instead of forcing data inside an analytical "cube", they were made to take "raw data" and "mine" them, as if data were some natural material. In order to analyse changes in the narratives going with the changes in technical tools, I have focused on published research in Computer Science fields dedicated to data (management, processing, mining...), probing the ability of prominent conferences in applied research to act as promissory organisations (Pollock & Williams, 2010). In short, data mining has been along all the 2000's, data scales and become big after 2010, and in 2012, the academia suddenly becomes tired of "mining" and switches to (machine) "learning". Then, twenty years after data warehouses were trendy, data lakes become mainstream.

Scaling up success stories: stabilizing an innovation economy in the face of pervasive instability in Jordan *Christian Haddad, Austrian Institute for International Affairs - oiip*

What are the stakes in establishing a scalable, innovation-driven economy in a country constantly haunted by pervasive instability? Building on a recently completed research project on sociotechnical visions of innovation in the Middle East and North Africa, the paper attends to the narratives of key actors invested in Jordan's future as a country of innovation. Situated in a region of geopolitical turmoil that has repeatedly shaken by multiple crises, Jordan is aspiring to become part of a thriving global knowledge economy. Recently, it has seen a dynamic development of its innovation ecosystem. Success stories such as those of Maktoob – an Arabic content app bought by Yahoo for USD 175m in 2009 – have become a generative myth of the power of entrepreneurship and innovation that can be unleashed in and for Jordan. Yet, the crucial challenge that remains up to today is how to scale up, to direct innovation towards measurable impacts and to establish a 'culture of innovation' in all sectors of society. Drawing on qualitative interviews and ethnographic observation in 2019, the paper situates the sociotechnical visions that drive innovation policy in the Hashemite Kingdom and explores how actors seek to multiply volatile success stories, thereby problematizing individual, institutional and structural constraints and 'innovation deficits' in Jordan. Adding to STS

work on innovation imaginaries, the paper examines some of the implicit notions of innovation and/in crisis at work in a post-colonial country marked by a sense of constant geopolitical and economic instability and a silent fear of pending breakdown.

Temporal tensions of dynamic capabilities: The integration of large-scale, external resources and the implications of assetization for non-profit hybrid organizations *Jane Bjørn Vedel, Copenhagen Business School; Kean Birch, York University*

The literature on dynamic capabilities takes assets as givens, leaving the processes through which organizational assets are created and integrated under-explored. In this paper, we argue that the contingent socio-material practices of diverse organizational actors are implicated in the transformation of external resources into organizational assets – defined as a process of assetization. Based on an extensive, qualitative study of large-scale, long-term grants awarded to professors in universities in a northern European context, we show that professors integrate external resources as organizational assets through the processes of framing, calculating, and managing. Following from this, we show that the integration of resources as assets results in temporal tensions, associated with the temporariness, temporal rhythms, and time horizons of these external resources. These findings advance our theoretical understanding of dynamic capabilities by emphasizing the assetization and temporal tensions inherent to the management of large-scale resources and assets. Moreover, they provide a window into the organizational implications of scaling up in the context of higher education.

Session Organizer:

Sebastian Michael Pfothenauer, Technical University Munich

365. Canadian Science = Settler Science - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

This session explores the multitude of ways that colonial, settler science in Canada masquerades as democratic, and how some Indigenous and non-Indigenous actors are unsettling what counts as 'Canadian' science. Technoscientific institutions and practices are a primary modality through which the settler colonial state inflicts violence, and this violence is enacted both materially and epistemically. We suggest that technoscientific practice—be it microbiology, genomics, demography, fisheries, mining, forestry, or data science and AI—continues to do the work of the contemporary colonial state in Canada by reinforcing colonial hierarchies and exclusion, legitimating capitalist extraction, propping up liberal ideas of multiculturalism and diversity, and enabling cultural genocide. This panel also addresses Canadian scientific and innovation infrastructure—tri-council funding agencies and academic and federal science—to consider how funding and research structures enable the ongoing exclusion and marginalization of Indigenous knowledges and practices. We invite contributions from scholars exploring a range of technoscientific practices, actors, and areas of expertise in the Canadian context to examine the national politics of transnational technoscience in the settler state. How has settler science worked to delegitimize Indigenous-led projects? How can we remake technoscientific methods in order to move toward caring, good relations? We seek papers that offer empirically grounded analyses of the relations and material practices that make up settler science. By examining the ways in which Canadian technoscience might be unsettled and decolonized, we aim to facilitate urgently-needed conversations in STS on the possibilities for challenging the persistent colonial work of Canadian scientific projects.

Participants:

Desktop Prospecting and Citizen Extractivism *Tom Ozden-Schilling, Johns Hopkins University*

In recent years, government-run geological surveys have increasingly facilitated exploration for potential mines by inviting novice prospectors to sift through old datasets prior to visiting physical sites. In northern British Columbia, Canada,

some novices have developed sophisticated techniques for analyzing promising “signs” in these data and narrativizing their own “desktop prospecting” labor within broader environmental and economic shifts playing out across rural Canada. Following recent calls to investigate numbers and numeracy as an “inventive frontier” (Guyer et al. 2010) for anthropological theory, this article examines how government efforts to vernacularize geological expertise is transforming the ways rural residents leverage emergent statistical knowledge in local debates over speculation and extraction. I draw on ethnographic encounters with retired mining engineers and other desktop prospectors who participated in a recent “data literacy” campaign undertaken by GeoscienceBC, an NGO established to encourage companies to search for new ore bodies within historic mining regions. Through the campaign, GeoscienceBC promoted web-based data visualization tools alongside recently produced geotechnical datasets obtained through aerial surveys. With free maps and simple analytical software in hand, the NGO argued, individual prospectors could play critical roles in cultivating new senses of economic possibility around northern British Columbia’s remote landscapes, and potentially lure mineral exploration companies back to the region after a decades-long decline in mining activity. By tracking these promises through online exchanges and everyday conversations, this article examines how rural residents’ demands for new data and tools are reshaping the limits of “citizen science” in a resurgent extractive regime.

Frontier Fantasies of Biodiversity: How the Framework of ‘Intactness’ Enables Extractive Industry *Sarah Blacker, York University*

This paper examines how the Alberta Biodiversity Monitoring Institute (ABMI) produces biodiversity data that can be mobilized to make ongoing colonial extraction possible in Alberta, Canada. The ABMI has developed a “biodiversity intactness index,” through which biodiversity data collected can be aggregated in ways that suggest that biodiversity in Alberta is largely “intact,” despite the existence of data pointing to the catastrophic scale of contamination wrought by the oil industry. I explore the role that the framework of “intactness” can play in obfuscating evidence of harm wrought by industry and in enabling colonial extraction projects to proceed with impunity. The pervasiveness of the “intactness” framework advances settler science by obscuring the colonial violence inherent in the industrial contamination of Indigenous communities. In doing so, the “intactness” framework interrupts public discourse on industrial “pollution as colonialism” (Liboiron 2017, 2021). I argue that framing biodiversity as “intact” does not only enable colonial extractive industry to continue by satisfying international environmental monitoring organizations’ standards; this method of data production and interpretation also counters Indigenous Traditional Ecological Knowledge (TEK) as part of a larger settler project to delegitimize data produced by Indigenous-led community monitoring projects in the province. Extending STS scholarship on how settler colonialism enables environmental violence (Shadaan and Murphy 2020), I show how “intactness” is being mobilized as a new iteration and continuation of the terra nullius doctrine that aims to cement settler control over land and resources while obscuring and marginalizing Indigenous refusals of settler science and industry.

Oil & Gas “Clean-tech”, Blue-collar Workers, and Settler Sociotechnical Imaginaries *Alana Lajoie O’Malley, University of Ottawa*

In this paper I explore the coproduction of government-supported science aimed at “greening” the oil and gas sector and ongoing formations of settler-colonialism in Canada. Drawing on financial documents and analysis of federal innovation and climate change plans and policies, I detail government investments in research on oil and gas “clean-tech” both in terms of dollars spent and in terms of policy commitments made. I go

on to relate these investments to the sociotechnical imaginaries on display when governments and pipeline companies are confronted with Indigenous refusals of their projects. I highlight the ways government investments in technoscientific innovation in oil and gas rely on the reproduction of a settler-colonial social order and vice versa. In particular, I examine the “blue-collar oil and gas worker” as both an imagined and a material actor whose needs and wants both require and justify Canada’s jurisdictional claims over unceded lands and whose continued existence requires investment in particular kinds of science and innovation. Ultimately, I argue that government investments in oil and gas research cannot be understood separately from processes that enroll “blue-collar oil and gas workers” into the work of reproducing settler-colonial dynamics. These processes of enrollment include the cultivation of settler attachment to place, the ritualistic retelling of stories about progress and innovation that cannot be separated from these attachments to place, and the cultivation of social identities associated with specific technoscientific infrastructures.

The Social Life of Fraser River Sockeye: Salmon Controversies in the Cohen Commission and Beyond *Callum C J Sutherland, York University*

This paper brings feminist and postcolonial STS to bear on a virtual analysis of the “social life” (Appadurai, 1986; Kopytoff, 1986; Dumit, 2004) of Fraser River sockeye salmon with the aim of shedding light on the foregrounding or backgrounding of particular forms of evidence in the Cohen Commission. Established in 2009, the Commission was tasked with investigating the decline of sockeye salmon in the Fraser River of British Columbia, Canada. In 2012, the Commission released the Cohen Report, which begins with an overview of the life cycle of sockeye. In this paper, I ask: What salmon controversies are revealed in this life-cycle overview, and how do they compare to those revealed by the social life of sockeye? To address this question, I arrayed ethnographic and interview data onto a custom map, which I then used to follow Fraser sockeye from their spawning grounds to the Pacific Ocean and back again. Along the way, I paused at numerous junctures to consider what, if anything, the Cohen Report has to say about the salmon controversies encountered there. This analysis demonstrates, I suggest, that the Cohen Report disregards Indigenous perspectives in reducing the sockeye life-cycle to a series of physiological transformations loosely connected to place. By privileging Indigenous perspectives, I argue, the social life of sockeye shows that the lives of these fish are also defined by myriad social transformations which derive meaning from the particulars of the places through which they travel, and the actors with whom they interact along the way.

Session Organizers:

Denielle a Elliott, York University
Sarah Blacker, York University

Chair:

Denielle a Elliott, York University

Discussant:

Karen Hebert, Carleton University

366. NSF Funding Opportunities for Science and Technology Studies Research

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

NSF Program Directors will discuss funding opportunities of interest to STS scholars as well as ways to find NSF funding opportunities and to become a reviewer. The presentation will focus on NSF STS Program as well as cross directorate programs and initiatives such as Ethical and Responsible Research, Dynamics of Integrated Socio-Environmental Systems, and NSF Research Traineeship. In addition, the Program Directors will answer questions about NSF policies, best practices in preparing proposals, being a reviewer, post-award responsibilities and other

NSF related questions.

Session Organizers:

Frederick M. Kronz, The National Science Foundation

Wenda K Bauchspies, MSU, GenCen

Chair:

Wenda K Bauchspies, MSU, GenCen

367. Transforming the Development & Governance of Pharmaceuticals - IV

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Major changes are underway within the pharmaceutical sector that are associated with shifts in research, innovation and business models from blockbuster products intended for large patient populations to more niche products designed for smaller, more targeted populations. Innovation is underway in how drugs are being researched and developed, and how they are being manufactured, used, evaluated, licensed and paid for. While some of these changes are tied to genomics and the rise of personalized medicine, others result of patient activism and disease politics. These technical and political developments put pressure on public regulators and payers, resulting in novel forms of governance, including the use of real world data and conditional reimbursement. This panel builds on STS scholarship on the socio-technical production of pharmaceutical knowledge, as well as its material and biopolitical impacts. We invite papers from a range of international perspectives that critically analyze these transformations, as well as those that highlight forms of alternative pharmaceutical practices and methods that are more sustainable and offer more just and equitable access to treatments. Topics may include but are not limited to: – Forms of open pharmaceutical innovation – Industry dynamics and changing business models – Patient groups and new forms of knowledge production – R&D partnerships across public, not-for-profit and/or private sector – Drug repurposing and off-label use – Changing regulatory knowledge and forms of evaluation – Pharmaceutical pricing and access – Novel access arrangement and alternative regulatory frameworks for coverage – Future health care system sustainability and social solidarity.

Participants:

Digital Governance of Public Health: Towards a Regulatory Framework for Internet Pharmacies *Aria Ilyad Ahmad, Dahdaleh Institute for Global Health Research*

To address the rising cost of medical products, patients and policymakers have increasingly turned to alternative marketplaces, such as internet pharmacies. When internet pharmacies are credentialed (i.e. operating within established legal/regulatory standards) evidence suggests they can significantly improve medicine access and affordability. Despite the potential public health benefits, regulation of internet pharmacies remains underdeveloped. In contrast to the jurisdictional development of medicine regulation, the internet's distributed nature alongside information asymmetries associated with diffuse transnational supply chains present unique challenges to internet pharmacies. Meanwhile, 'rogue' internet marketplaces (i.e. operating outside legal/regulatory standards) can amplify public health risks and undermine intellectual property rights. Applying an ethnographic approach to historic institutionalism, this paper will excavate the resulting 'patchwork' of regulatory approaches to internet pharmacies, anchored by the complementary theories of regulatory regimes and intermediary governance. While the latter illuminates the growing role of internet intermediaries in policing online content and behaviour, regime theory is a useful analytic framework to examine the emergence and enforcement of regulatory arrangements from technical design of the internet architecture and resource coordination, to private ordering and conflicts at control points. Emphasizing the regulatory hybridity of internet governance, the paper interrogates the overlapping state-corporate actors advancing formal-informal regulatory measures to internet pharmacies. While arguing that the resulting patchwork of private and often discretionary and non-legally

binding regulatory regimes increasingly undermine medicine access and public health, the paper surveys emerging polycentric and multi-stakeholder approaches to norm-based rule-making, including the 'Brussels Principles for the Sale of Medicines Over the Internet'.

Molecular Sovereignties – Patients, Genomes, And The Enduring Biocoloniality Of Intellectual Property *Eva Hilberg*

Monoclonal antibodies are revolutionizing cancer treatments, but come at an increasingly problematic price for health services worldwide. This leads to pressing demands for access, as in the case of Kadcyla. In 2015, patients in the United Kingdom invoked the sovereign rights of the Crown in order to demand access to this expensive yet potentially life-saving medicine that had prior been de-listed due to price. This article interprets this campaign as an act of sovereign reassertion against a fundamental exclusion, which however ultimately fails to challenge the concrete mechanism enabling this exclusion – intellectual property (IP). By connecting this example to other declarations of molecular sovereignty, the article argues that the use of sovereignty can perpetuate further exclusion. Drawing on the notion of biocoloniality (Schwartz-Marín and Restrepo 2013) it points out that the intellectual property regime contains a deeply embedded fiction of the world as terra nullius, a blank uninhabited canvas ripe for discovery and appropriation. This decontextualised vision of life as property works to exclude populations and patients from playing a significant role in determining the use of technologies and treatments. Instead of countering this fundamental exclusion, the concept of sovereignty further entrenches this assumption and merely contests the assignation of this property. The paper seeks to contribute to discussions surrounding drug pricing by analysing existing patient activism in a field that otherwise often excludes their voice.

The Evolution and Dynamics of the Orphan Drug Innovation in the US *Jin Ding, University of Sheffield; Robin Williams, The University of Edinburgh; Alessandro Rossiello, University of Edinburgh*

Drugs for treating rare diseases were neglected by the pharmaceutical industry for a long time, due to the small unprofitable market and the complex drug R&D process. The Orphan Drug Act (ODA) has sought to address the health inequality of rare diseases by reducing the regulatory and economic barriers. The number of orphan drugs available in the market has risen sharply from about ten in the decade before 1983 to over 900 until 2020. This increase implies a substantial improvement in the healthcare of patients suffering rare diseases and the success of the orphan drug legislation. The high price of orphan drugs has attracted more companies to develop drugs in the area of rare diseases, but it limited the patient access to treatments. The dilemma presented by the ODA reflects many of the issues currently faced by policymakers. By combining the theory of the sectoral system of innovation and complex adaptive system, this paper models the long-term dynamics and evolution of the orphan drug innovation system by Multi-agent based simulation. The model investigates the roles of the main players in the sector and their relationships embedded in the process of orphan drug innovation. Through this model, the mechanisms of how the incentives stimulate orphan drug innovation during the period from 1983- 2020 are explored. Moreover, the model is applied to solve the dilemma of the ODA through analyzing how to achieve the best trade-off between the innovation of orphan drugs and the affordability of treatments.

What is a stimulant drug? Some thoughts on the constitution of categories of psychotropic drugs in biomedical psychiatry *Lauren Predebon, Universidad de la República (Uruguay)*

How do categories of psychotropic drugs emerge and evolve? What role do the naming choice for a group of drugs play in how

sickness, health and wellbeing are perceived? This paper explores such questions by looking into the stimulants (methylphenidate, modafinil etc). Being one of the five conventional groups of psychotropic drugs - along with antidepressants, anxiolytics, antipsychotics and mood stabilizers - the name "stimulants" presents a particular case for some reasons: 1) unlike the aforementioned categories, it does not indicate the targeted disorder; 2) the word "stimulants" can also refer to other kinds of substances (e.g. illegal drugs); 3) it can be a puzzling name when the consumer group includes overstimulated ADHD patients. Nevertheless, "stimulants" was one of the first classifications of psychotropic drugs (Moncrieff, 2008) and remains relevant. This paper approaches the ways in which the stimulants became consolidated as a category of psychotropic drugs. Some of them are: the contrast with other drug categories, the conditions they mean to treat (which have evolved too) and the theories regarding their action on mental processes. Such has led to a number of changes throughout the years, even without major molecule breakthroughs. The success of the stimulants includes repurposing and also expanding beyond the limits of a mental disorder, raising regulation debates. Hence, this study exemplifies the basis on which psychiatric drugs are constituted, used and marketed, impacting the ways intimate feelings are perceived and approached. This paper is part of an ongoing study about user experiences of stimulant drugs in Uruguay.

Session Organizers:

Conor Douglas, York University

Paul Martin, Department of Sociological Studies, University of Sheffield

Tineke Kleinhout-Vliek, Copernicus Institute of Sustainable Development, Utrecht University

Chair:

Conor Douglas, York University

368. Critical Computing: Practicing Collective Agency in the Tech World

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Science and Technology Studies has a rich literature critiquing computing / computer science as a discipline. Yet, there remains a strong disconnect between STS and computing: practitioners have a history of dismissing STS for a variety of reasons such as inaccessibility and technical naiveté --- and being unaware of improvements within STS on these fronts. In this panel we discuss how STS can move further beyond critique, through developing new methodologies and creating a "successor science" of computing (Harding 1986). This panel contributes to STS through showcasing sites of collaboration between STS and computing practitioners, and the resulting methodologies that emerge. This builds on works at these intersections (e.g. Suchman 1993, Agre 1995) and continues conversation from previous 4S conferences (e.g. "Crafting Critical Methodologies in Computing" panel in 2020). We continue to trouble notions of outsider and insider in computing, and what it means to be a computer scientist. This panel will be guided by the following central questions: - How can STS be both critical and constructive of computing? - What are the highest-leverage ways to change computing toward more just and sustainable practices? - How can we engage computing practitioners with ideas and insights from STS, such as crip technoscience and cyborg feminism? - How can critical thought/theory inform methodology building in computing? How can interactions between (feminist, postcolonial, crip, queer) STS and computing establish new methodological considerations?

Participants:

Empathy has never been enough — Humility as a Guiding Principle for Participatory Design *Katta Spiel, TU Wien; Gopinath Kannabiran, ITU Copenhagen*

Empathy is hailed as a core competency of participatory design (PD) and key to a deep understanding of nuanced experiences people make with technologies (Wright & McCarthy, 2008).

However, such an approach remains disengaged from the power dynamics at the core PD projects. Researchers and practitioners deciding the frame of participation and taking upon themselves the core responsibilities for shaping the engagements, even when driven by a critical stance, often shy away from addressing these power issues explicitly (Bratteteig & Wagner, 2014). We argue that orienting our research practice through empathy can at times lead to unintentional detrimental consequences. Without a nuanced understanding of power dynamics, researchers are likely to centre their own understanding and relating to technological experiences over those of participants — with dire material consequences particularly for marginalised populations. In this context, we propose a guiding principle focused on humility at the core of participatory design to orient researchers and industry representatives on practices around 1) making space for participants' contributions, 2) listening to what is explicitly expressed and what is not, and 3) deliberately sharing the agency and meaning making process that is traditionally less in the hands of participants. For this, we need to proactively claim our privileged positions and deliberately learn to be humble about our contributions. Coming from this principle, we might create spaces in which we attend to participants with an interest in epistemic justice instead of habitually risking to override their experiences by filtering them through our own.

Disrupting Teacher Education for Computing *Elizabeth Patitsas, McGill University*

Education plays a significant role in shaping how people understand the purpose and boundaries of a discipline. Computer science is at a crossroads: its purpose is being debated internally when it comes to its professional and social responsibilities. Professionals have also been concerned with the shrinking demographic diversity of its members, generally without connecting the trend to how the field also has a history of drawing its boundaries to exclude subareas that are seen as more feminine. Computing education is hence an important lever for making change in the field. In this talk I will report on my experiences teaching a course on computing education that is informed by STS. The course attracts a mix of K-12 and university educators, both pre-service and in-service. I have taught the course three times at this point. I will reflect on the curriculum development process, and the shift from teaching computing education in a liberal, cognitivist framing to a critical, STS-informed one. I will share insights and pedagogical content knowledge for teaching STS to computing educators, such as the importance of giving them clear paths forward for (re)framing their own teaching; e.g. framing human-computer interaction around crip technoscience, framing resource management around Dish With One Spoon law, embedding history of computing in the curriculum. Finally, I argue for the importance of teacher education as a site for applying STS.

Working with Critical Conceptual Tools in Machine Learning Systems Design: Report From the Field *Goda Klumbyte, University of Kassel*

In the recent years computer science has developed sophisticated technical tools to improve machine learning accuracy and expand application fields, however, systemic socio-cultural bias remains a significant topic in machine learning systems. There is by now a plethora of resources that address such bias, some of them offering technical solutions, while others taking more structural approaches based on the premise that more transparent, explainable, and understandable systems would be less biased. Critical theories, particularly feminist, postcolonial and anti-racist scholarship, have developed grounded methodological and conceptual tools to address societal bias and its embeddedness in systems of thought and technology, and to trace how these embeddings give rise to new and reproduce existing hierarchies of power in society. This paper will report on a series of workshops that explored interdisciplinary approaches to machine learning systems design by drawing on insights developed in

critical scholarship, specifically feminist, postcolonial and anti-racist scholarship and its methodologies. The workshops offered participants from human-computer interaction and machine learning space to experiment with the methods and concepts developed in social sciences & humanities research by applying them to machine learning systems design through a series of speculative design exercises. Specifically, concepts such as “figuration” (Haraway, Braidotti), “situating/situated knowledge” (Haraway, Hill Collins, Harding), “critical fabulation/speculation” (Hartman, Rosner) and “diffraction” (Barad) were used to help re-imagine machine learning systems design as a more contextualized, interdisciplinary process. This paper will offer some preliminary reflections on possibilities and challenges that emerged through conducting this workshop series.

Establishing Critique as a Political Mode in Requirements Engineering *Doris Allhutter, Austrian Academy of Sciences; Christoph Becker, University of Toronto*

Requirements Engineering (RE) is a pivotal point where social perspectives get translated into technical specifications. Power relations and marginalization play an important role when choosing which boundaries to draw around the specification of system design criteria; which stakeholders to involve; which problem framing to pursue; and through many other decisions in requirements practice and theory. Presenting the results of an ethnographic study with a deconstructive approach, we elaborate on the epistemic norms that shape the relation between research and practice in the field. We make visible the boundary work implied by RE as an engineering field integrating social science approaches. The study locates a crucial moment of enacting power relations in the boundary work between the more technically-centered RE and ‘critical’ RE but also in the boundaries enacted between practitioners and researchers. Based on the empirical findings we develop a notion of critique as a relational mode amongst and between ‘epistemic communities’ and ‘communities of practice’ that establishes a political project of redirecting the differences enacted through structural power relations towards accountable collective agency. Searching for new imaginaries and transformative potentialities, new materialist scholars call for a less negative and more generative mode of critical engagement. However, as Bargetz and Sanos (2020: 503, Feminist Theory 21/4) remind us, it is crucial to address “how we might sustain a form of ... critical interrogation of the ways power functions and how its uses may subvert, unmoor and rework its operations in the political”.

Art/Science, History, and Speculative Design as Critical Technical Practices for Crisis Informatics *Robert Soden, University of Toronto*

ICTs such as mapping platforms, algorithms, and databases are a central component of how society understands and responds to the threats posed by disasters. However, these systems have come under increasing criticism in recent years for prioritizing knowledge produced by technical disciplines over insights from the humanities and social science and failing to adequately incorporate the priorities of vulnerable or affected communities. Drawing on Phil Agre's notion of critical technical practice and successive work in the field of human-computer interaction, I offer an argument for an updated vision of, critical technical practice for the field of crisis informatics that can better address the social context in which ICTs are developed and appropriated. Then, drawing on several case studies from ongoing projects related to earthquake modeling, hurricane risk communications, and flood early warning systems, I suggest that art/science collaboration, historical research, and speculative design can expand our repertoire of critical practices. Together, these practices increase the range of tactics that designers and researchers working on ICTs used in disasters can deploy when seeking to ensure their work contributes to safety, sustainability, and justice.

Session Organizers:

Elizabeth Patitsas, McGill University
Christoph Becker, University of Toronto
Robert Soden, University of Toronto

Chair:

Elizabeth Patitsas, McGill University

369. Data / Care: Relations, Affects, Practices - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

As digital data continues to rapidly proliferate, sustained by the ever-expanding architecture of the cloud, discussion of “data management” has become ubiquitous. Individuals, institutions, and states are all faced with the onerous work of organizing, culling, and keeping track of their data, raising questions that range from the stakes of self-archiving to the environmental costs of large-scale data storage (Hogan 2013). This panel proposes a new approach to these now-common problems, asking: does it make sense to talk about data care? When we center the people tasked with “managing” data in our analysis, questions of relationality inevitably arise. Is something like care at work when a data center technician sustains terabytes of data through his everyday practice, or saves it in the face of natural disaster? What kind of relating is at play in a researcher’s process of ensuring her data set is “clean”? What do intense affects associated with “data hoarding” and data loss tell us about normative expectations of care (Dow Schüll 2017)? By positing care as a flexible center point in this conversation, we aim to dig deeper into the relationships between people and the data they are responsible for. Topics of discussion may include, but are not limited to: - Design and maintenance of digital infrastructure - Questions of data privacy, ownership, and sovereignty - Non-human and new materialist approaches to data relations - Gendered histories and practices of data care Session I of this two-part panel is organized around “Data for Caring”; Session II is on “Caring for Data.”

Participants:

Data friction: Understanding data management as care work
Irina Zakharova, University of Bremen; Juliane Jarke, University of Bremen

The so-called datafication assumes the smooth flow of data within and across interoperable data infrastructures. However, far from flowing smoothly, such “data journeys” (Bates et al. 2016, Leonelli 2020) include friction and unaccomplished movements. In order to better understand data friction, we propose to examine data management as care work and data as part of an organisation’s care arrangement. For that, we build on Tronto’s (1993) feminist ethics of care and the posthumanist approach to care by Puig de la Bellacasa (2017). The care arrangements which produce data are made up of various, interrelated elements like data sharing infrastructures (such as information systems, technical infrastructure); socio-cultural factors (such as the care dispositions of various social actors) and regulatory frameworks (such as policies and legal frameworks). At times however, these elements restrict or hinder movement. For datasets to sustain, the onerous practices of data management and tending to data are required. In our contribution, we draw on a study that examines school management systems in public schools in four federal states of Germany. The study is based on interviews with school actors such as principals, teachers, secretaries, and IT managers, as well as school management systems’ designers. Attending analytically to data friction allows to uncover care practices of repairing, maintaining and continuing data management. In so doing, data management can be conceived as enabling new modes of care with, through and against technology and data.

Critical Care for the Early Web: Ethical Approaches to Archived Youth Data *Katie Mackinnon*

The Early Internet Memories project explores personal and public archives that contain web materials made by young people throughout 1994-2005 through qualitative, online semi-structured interviews. Participants are positioned as co-investigator and analyst of web archival material, enabling simultaneous

discovery, memory, interpretation and investigation, as they guide the researcher through a walkthrough of their digital materials collected and stored in web archives (Light, Burgess, Duguay, 2016; Robards & Lincoln, 2017). This paper demonstrates an ethico-methodological (Cowan, 2020) approach to working with archived web pages created by young people and emerged out of a desire to develop a framework of care for engaging with web history that acknowledges ethical gaps in internet research. One of the main challenges to researching historical web archives is grappling with distance between researchers and the researched; websites become defunct, users have grown up and changed names, and communities have splintered and dispersed. Informed consent is nearly never a possibility, and while deploying “contextual integrity” tactics and evaluating the scale of archived web materials are significant ethical developments (Lomborg, 2018; Nissenbaum, 2010; Tiinderberg, 2018), getting in contact with creators of digital materials is still an important ethical dimension for many internet researchers (Eichhorn, 2019; Horbinski, 2018; Leurs 2017; Lialina, 2017; Robards & Lincoln, 2020). The adapted guided walkthrough method that I developed is also influenced by the conceptual framing of data materials in research on the “right to be forgotten” (Crossen-White, 2015; GDPR, 2018; Tsesis, 2014), digital afterlives (Sutherland, 2020), indigenous data sovereignty and governance (Wemigwans, 2018), and the Feminist Data Manifest-No (Cifor et al, 2019). By exploring experiences and memories of the web in web archival research, we are able to re-center human and move towards a digital justice approach (Giesecking, 2020; Cowan & Rault, 2020) and a critical feminist ethics of care (Luka & Millette, 2018) for engaging with historical youth data.

“Fringes” Between Fields: Re-Examining Invisible Work And Marginality In Cultural Heritage *Quoc-Tan Tran, University of Hamburg*

The politics of “caring for objects” remains at the heart of the information and technical work of GLAM (galleries, libraries, archives, and museums) institutions. Though often regarded as sort of “ordinarily invisible” (Bowker & Star, 1999) activities, or the “fringes” between fields (Star, 2002), documentation work keeps the institutional fabric from fragmenting in ways that could encourage user’s mistrust and disengagement. Drawing on staff interviews and ethnographic fieldwork conducted at the Museum of European Cultures (MEK)—Berlin’s National Museums, this paper explores the limits and fragility of caring concerning what I call the “caring tasks”, i.e., everyday doings that staff need to perform to avoid any detriment to the institution’s functioning and its objects. The social dimension of care provides a plausible way to understand collections documentation as maintaining “the webs of relationality” (Puig de la Bellacasa, María, 2010) that are formed among humans, non-human agents, and objects. The case of “Category 74” in the MEK’s category system—initially used for photographs but in fact covers everything born-digital and newly digitized materials—shows how standardized tools and procedures at the core of knowledge representation relegate essential entities to the periphery. The appearance of the “fringes” could be subtle, their use is insecure and precarious, and the work on themselves could be easily treated as taken-for-granted. These aspects, nevertheless, offer valuable other layers of narratives. The “fringes” could be far from the center but definitively not hard to reach. They are, and will be, affected by our action.

Farming the Cloud: Animacy, Vitalism, and Metabolic Metaphor in Data Centers *Steven Gonzalez, MIT*

Referred to interchangeably as “server farms”, data centers – cloud infrastructures that store digital content – are of increasing interest to scholars (Amoore 2018, Cubitt 2016, Ensmenger 2017, Johnson 2014, 2018, Holt and Vonderau 2015, Hogan 2018, Mosco 2010, Moro 2020, Starosielski 2016, Taylor 2018, Velkova 2016, Vonderau 2018). Given the immense volume of

electricity, water, and other environmental resources consumed by data storage infrastructures, it is not metaphorical to refer to data centers as “farms” and servers as “crops”. In this paper, I contend that such a framing has real analytical purchase in empirical contexts. Drawing on ethnographic research in data centers among server technicians, I present a range of behaviors and linguistic formations that empirically further the resonance of the cloud as a species of “farm”. My ongoing research illustrates how metabolic and animistic metaphors structure relations between computer servers and the technicians charged with their care. In the speech habits of technicians, I locate a persistent vitalist quality that pervades talk about servers. As evidenced by interview transcripts, servers are variously framed by technicians as “hungry”, “tired”, or “moody”. Additionally, I document how particular servers are treated as individuals replete with specific names and personalities to distinguish them from others in their “flocks” (Orr 1996). I conclude with a provisional analysis that brings new materialist, material-semiotic, and linguistic anthropological approaches into conversation (Durham Peters 2015, Haraway 2015, Helmreich 2009, Silvio 2010, Wark 2015).

‘Just Infrastructure’: Logics and Labors of Data Center Care *Alix Johnson, University of Florida*

Based on twenty months of ethnographic research at and around data centers in Iceland, this paper interrogates data center developers’ and technicians’ relationships to the data their work supports. While these interlocutors acknowledged the high stakes of their labors – for example, rushing to the data center in advance of a snowstorm to work against the possibility of remote clients losing access – they routinely disavowed the kind of affective investment that might be classified as “care.” Instead, they deployed the frameworks of infrastructural “maintenance” and “security” to describe the actions they take on data’s behalf. Toggling between the everyday activities inside a data center, and the town of Reykjanesbær where it is located, this paper suggests that while these male-dominated workspaces make little room for an explicit claiming of care, care for data has nevertheless been integral to creating and sustaining the industry in Southern Iceland. It is less visible at the most immediate interfaces with data, than in the surrounding community where this concern has been deferred. In Reykjanesbær, I argue that a compulsory care toward others’ data has been one of the social and spatial costs of data center development.

Data Work: The Hidden Labor Ecologies of Amazon Data Workers *Lauren E Bridges, Annenberg School of Communication, University of Pennsylvania*

Amazon is the earth’s largest online retailer and cloud computing provider, the second largest employer in the United States, and one of the most economically unequal workforces in existence. This inequity is embedded throughout Amazon’s data infrastructures, which renders some bodies and communities as valuable and discards others as expendable. Largely hidden from the customer, Amazon relies on an array of data workers who produce, interact with, care for, maintain, store, and handle physical data objects to ensure the efficient flow of goods through Amazon’s supply chain and work to protect the continued production of ‘data rents’ through Amazon’s cloud services. This paper asks, what are the embodied experiences of working with and for data? I explore this question through textual and visual analysis of online narrative accounts of what it is like to work in two different segments of Amazon’s business: warehouses and data centers to understand how workers relate to and work with, in, and through data infrastructures. I hypothesize that data work has different embodied lived experience depending one’s proximity to the data center where the rippling effects of bodily impacts propagate outwardly the further one moves from the center.

Session Organizers:

Alix Johnson, University of Florida

Steven Gonzalez, MIT

370. Evidence-based Medicine? Regulating Vaccines, Drugs and Other Health Products during COVID 19 and Beyond-II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

AS 2021 Virtual: 18

Facing an untamed pandemic, governments have leveraged public trust and perhaps health in facilitating good relations with industry in co-producing innovative health products in record time. Established evidence-based medicine standards have been overshadowed by the deployment of new regulatory mechanisms such as Emergency Use Authorizations (in the US and UK), Interim Orders (Canada), and Conditional Marketing Authorizations (European Union) that have expedited Covid19 diagnostics, therapeutics, and vaccines to an anxious public, despite partial and uncertain clinical trial “results.” To unpack this trend, which capitalized upon pre-pandemic social alliances and regulatory modernization agendas that emphasize agility, flexibility and innovation, and its impact upon the future of health product regulatory practices, papers in this session will address one or more of the following lines of inquiry: • Investigating the shifts in regulatory approaches, practices, and responses that confirm or counter the perceived erosion in evidence-based appraisal of health products; • Offering theoretical, empirical and especially ethnographic findings that characterize the political economy or structural drivers of the changes in health product governance before and/or during the pandemic, and their implications for post-pandemic futures; • Attending to new modes of biopharmaceutical knowledge production, including alternative therapies, such as psychedelic-assisted therapies, that disrupt entrenched relations between regulators and ‘big pharma’ in the wake of Covid19 and evolving standards of safety and effectiveness. Engaging with critical analyses of how knowledge and evidence is shaped by powerful vested interests, such as the pharmaceutical industry, the session will contribute to STS scholarship on regulatory governance.

Participants:

A Critical Political Economy Perspective on the Health Product Regulatory Authorities’ Responses to COVID-19 Pandemic
Ipek Eren Vural, Dalhousie University

Regulatory reviews conducted by health products authorities, such as Health Canada (HC), European Medicines Agency (EMA), formed a crucial part of the global public health response to COVID-19 pandemic. Regulatory reviews weigh in competing goals of health product regulation, such as protecting the public from unknown safety risks of the novel health care products, allowing patients timely access to life-saving therapies, and rewarding the private sector’s pharma, biotech, and medical device investments for future innovations. The competing goals of health product regulation are embedded in the contradictions between the accumulation and legitimation objectives of the liberal democratic states in capitalist economies and correspond to different societal interests, such as those of the industry, citizens, and the public. COVID-19 global public health crisis intensified the tensions between the competing goals of health product regulation. In response, health care product authorities adopted various contradictory and complementary strategies to overcome the increased stakes in their decisions. The term “competitive interdependence” is used here to refer to such strategies. These range from national health product regulatory authorities’ increased reliance on each other to share the risks of their regulatory decisions to their intense competition against each other to attract greater number of sponsors’ product submissions and allow timely access of their populations to COVID 19 therapies and vaccines. Drawing on primary data from interviews with Health Canada officials, the review of official documents, and news articles, the paper seeks to expand work in STS that explore how social and structural relations shape regulatory responses.

Criticisms of EBM and their Limits: the Cases of AI in Radiology and Interventional Radiology
Léo Mignot, Université de Bordeaux - Centre Emile Durkheim

The Covid crisis has made the debates and criticisms surrounding evidence based medicine (EBM) particularly visible following the media coverage of scientific controversies concerning ongoing clinical trials. In order to better grasp the increasing criticism of EBM, we propose here to shift the focus from the pharmaceutical industry to the evaluation of other types of medical devices. More specifically, we propose to focus on two fields of investigation: applications of artificial intelligence (AI) in radiology and the development of interventional radiology (IR). Doing so allows us to bring out other forms of reproaches addressed by practitioners to EBM, but also to understand the strategies of professional valorization which underlies it. For that purpose we observed 130 IR operations and conducted more than 100 interviews with radiologists, researchers, medical industry actors and representatives of evaluation institutions. While clinical counting and evaluation practices existed in the past, the rise of EBM occurred mainly in the 20th century and accompanied the rise of the pharmaceutical industry (Daly, 2005; Marks, 1999; Timmermans and Berg, 2003). Because of this, the actors met are tempted to question EBM standards: they were based on the prism of drug substances regulation and cannot be immediately transposed to the evaluation of interventional medical techniques or to AI applications. We propose to analyze the arguments defended by the actors but also to show that meeting EBM standards is still a major issue for the legitimacy of medical specialties and their recognition by public authorities. This explains why, despite criticism, EBM remains central to the process of regulating medical activity.

The shifting regulatory landscape of global health: Knowledge and temporality in the management of global health emergencies
Michael Rabi, The Hebrew University of Jerusalem

For global health actors, a core problem in the governance of emergencies is about optimizing and calibrating now to allow a rapid response in future emergencies. In this paper, I draw on my ongoing ethnographic fieldwork in a European global health network (2017-) to investigate changes in health product governance in the context of global health and emergencies. Based on my analysis, I suggest that a link exists between current trends in health product governance (e.g. Emergency Use Authorization) and established global health emergency governance mechanisms. These mechanisms, I argue, involve strategies that are based on knowledge from the fields of emergency and disaster management. As such, they seek to enhance response rapidity in emergencies by forming alliances and strong ties between actors and cutting through red tape. As these strategies practically turn into the modus operandi of emergency management in global health, however, they also affect and reshape the regulatory landscape of this field. Focusing on (Europe-based) global health actors’ logistical mobilization of health products for operational interventions in emergencies prior to and during the 2020 Coronavirus pandemic, I show how knowledge and technologies that enable the realization of, and preparation towards emergencies in global health are determinative of regulatory developments in this regard. Further, I engage with science and technology studies and critical studies of global health and discuss the power dynamics at play in the relationship between knowledge, regulation, and temporality in the governance of global health and global health emergencies.

Session Organizer:

Agnieszka Doll, Dalhousie University

Chair:

Janice Graham, Dalhousie University

Discussant:

Matthew Herder, Director, Health Law Institute, Associate Professor, Faculties of Medicine and Law, Dalhousie University

371. Logics of anticipation II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

TBD, emphasis on communication

Participants:

Citizen Science in Times of Emergency: Brazilian Initiatives in Face of the Covid-19 Pandemic *Sarita Albagli, IBICT Brazilian Institute for Information in Science and Technology; Luana Mendonça Pinto Rocha, IBICT - Brazilian Institute of Information in Science and Technology*

This paper presents results of a research about the possibilities and limits of citizen science approaches and methods in coping with socio-environmental and sanitary disaster and emergency situations. It focused on the covid-19 “syndemic” (Horton, 2020), defined as a biological disaster with technological, social, and environmental dimensions (Rodrigues et al., 2020). Besides literature review, 71 citizen initiatives, developed in Brazil during the covid-19 outbreak in 2020, were analyzed and grouped into three categories: data and information; citizen “making”; solidarity and assistance support networks. The mapped initiatives were oriented both to promote citizen engagement and action in facing the covid-19, and to mobilize collective intelligence for the design of solutions to the crisis. Mutual learning was observed between citizen science methods of information and data collection, and participatory approaches to disaster risk resilience and response. The study also pointed out the relevance of reconceptualizing the epistemic framework of citizen science (Hicks et al., 2019) by taking into account the widening of its meaning and scope, beyond the contribution of non-specialists to stricto sensu scientific research projects, in order to face the growing number and amplitude of socio-environmental and sanitary disaster and emergency situations. Finally the survey suggests the need to consider the different technical background and epistemic bases between the variety of actors that promote these initiatives -- academic institutions, NGOs, startups with social interests, maker groups, community organizations and voluntary groups – which may imply hierarchical positions in the knowledge production systems, and thus unequal relationships in collaboration between them.

Disaster education for tackling black swans *Hideyuki Shiroshita, Kansai University*

After the 2011 Tohoku earthquake disaster, even the experts on disaster risk reduction started to use the word 'black swan' that means an unimaginable event to describe the disaster. Since then, tackling black swans has become one of the main issues of DRR. However, it is theoretically impossible to find black swans since if it is found before disaster strikes, it is not an unimaginable event but an expected event. The main problem related to the black swans is a misunderstanding of the black swans among the stakeholders. The situation that not all stakeholders understand the event as a black swan should be avoided. This misunderstanding would develop conflict among the stakeholders. And the term 'black swan' becomes an excuse of the people who do not know or do not appreciate the black swan in advance for those who recognise the black swan in advance. After disasters, many legal actions against governments have been repeated. The 2011 disaster is not an exception. The governments decide on a policy using the cutting edge of science, and the government officials think disasters are black swans, however, the residents have a different idea. How disaster education contributes to avoiding this conflict. From the conceptual study, it can be said not knowledge transmission but collaboration among stakeholders tackle black swans. In this presentation, disaster education is classified into three categories, and it is illustrated that collaboration is essential for all three types of disaster education.

Legacies of the Chikungunya crisis (2005-2006) in the local public health agency of La Réunion Island *Kamil GHOUATI,*

INRAE, LISIS

It is generally considered that public management of health risks in France owes a form of resilience to a long history of anticipation. However, the so-called Chikungunya crisis, the chemical control of mosquitoes and the mobilization dynamic that followed in Reunion Island between 2005 and 2006 did not fail to affect the population, raise new fears and hopes and lay the foundations, for the local public health agency, for a partial renewal of the approach to epidemics. It is then up to us to understand what this period of tension has revealed about the anticipation logics really at work within this agency and how this crisis has put them to the test. Drawing on broader sociological research with mixed methods targeting biotechnological innovation in mosquito control, we examine the planning role assumed by the local agency on the island at the time of the crisis. To do so, we mainly analyze two corpuses gathered over the 2005-2006 period by the Réunionnais archive services: the files of the Regional Health Agency and relevant press extracts from the main local newspapers. We highlight: 1/ the conditions for the joint emergence of a strong social demand and the deployment by the administration of a crisis management system associated with a social mobilization unit, 2/ the feedback that takes place between the health risk management system and epidemic events, and 3/ from interviews conducted at the end of 2020, what the current management system, mobilized against Dengue and Covid-19, owes to the period 2005-2006.

Police Communication and the Pandemic *Sarah Young, Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam*

Emergency communications can be classified into a variety of sub-genres, falling under the larger domain of business communication. For instance, risk communication involves minimizing emergencies before they start through the dissemination of information about possible risks (Kostelnick, 2007); crisis communications involve addressing business-borne emergencies (Moon & Rhee, 2012), and disaster communications respond to and communicate typically natural disasters (National Institute of Disaster Management, 2014). One interesting thing about these types of communications is that they are often limited to a department or a group of individuals to provide the communication, and they are often short-term periods of communication. The COVID-19 pandemic has forced many emergency workers to operate in a state similar to what Agamben (2004) called the “state of exception” though, and this has created institution-wide, exceptional communication changes that radically alter the way people work. But, how exactly has the pandemic affected law enforcement’s communications? And what can this say about business communications during the pandemic in general? Based on a thematic analysis of qualitative interviews of law enforcement workers across Europe, I argue law enforcement communications during the pandemic have in changed in that (1) there are new best practices to reiterate; (2) communication requires increased work due to increasing demands about crimes and training; and (3) potentials are more creative and open. This has created a feeling both of anxiety and hope in personnel, and there are hopes that the inclusion and acceptance to new ways of doing things persist even after the pandemic.

Session Organizer:

Sonja Schmid, Virginia Tech, Falls Church

372. Agrifood Futures in-the-Making: Part I

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

With a booming agritech sector, venture capitalists, philanthropists, scientists and engineers are playing an increasingly central role in shaping agrifood futures, both through the deployment of socio-technical imaginaries and the transformation of material realities. As a result, agrifood scholars are engaging with novel technologies including synthetic biology, tissue engineering, digitization, robotics, artificial intelligence and

related fields. Scholarship at the intersection of STS and agrifood studies allows for critical examination of the tensions between agritech's aspirations to radically transform farming and food systems, and the profound ecological and social consequences these transformations might entail. Papers in these four panels offer critical insights into contested agrifood futures in-the-making. Panels I and II will explore what it means to engineer both the 'perfect farm' and the 'perfect food.' Panels III and IV will discuss contested ideologies and ontologies of food, agriculture and technology. These panels highlight the work of scholars affiliated with the STS Food & Agriculture Network (STSFAN), a small but growing intellectual community. We also invite anyone interested in our work to join our conference Meetup to learn more about the network.

Participants:

Engineering land's financial future with digital technologies and big data *Sarah Ruth Sippel*

The nature of farming is – still – an essentially biological, and thus volatile, system which poses substantial challenges to its integration into financialized capitalism. Financial investors often seek stability and predictability of returns that are hardly compatible with agriculture – but which are increasingly seen as achievable via new digital farming technologies and big data. This paper explores how digital technologies are used 'on the ground' to engineer land's financial(ized) future. Drawing on qualitative fieldwork (interviews, participant observation) on financialized farms conducted in Australia between 2016 and 2019, I firstly show how farmland investors value, and promote, the automation and mechanization of farms to reduce and control labour. Secondly, I demonstrate how 'just-in-time' technologies are used to manage farms and information flows across large distances. I thirdly reveal how digital technologies are considered as a means to deliver the kind of 'objective' farm data requested by often urban-based investors with little or no experience in farming and agricultural investment. Digital technologies have become a key tool to transform farms into 'investment grade assets' endowed with rich data on farm performance and benefits. Financialization and digitization of farming can thus be seen as mutually reinforcing processes within the engineering of agrifood futures.

"Vertical Farms Solve Land Problem"? *Mark Bomford, Yale Sustainable Food Program*

This declaration (minus the question mark) headlined a CNN Money profile of Skygreens, one of the first commercial vertical farms. Vertical farming (VF) is a rapidly growing type of controlled environment agriculture (CEA) which has attracted widespread praise and considerable early-stage capital in recent years. Among VF's many claimed benefits, per-area productivity is most frequently mentioned, proposing crop yields that are at least two (and sometimes even three) orders of magnitude higher than outdoor field agriculture. Announcing itself as a promethean arrival at a moment of imminent global land scarcity disaster, VF occupies a place in rarefied upper reaches of the Borlaug hypothesis. Deeply embedded in sustainable agriculture discourse but rarely invoked by name, the Borlaug hypothesis proposes that deforestation, wilderness encroachment, and other large scale ecological impacts can be halted or reversed by concentrating high-yielding agriculture on hyper-productive land, "sparing" marginal farmland for nature. In a sensational articulation of this kind of intensification, VF proposes to stack CEA units on top of themselves, attaining yields so high that arable land will be rendered unnecessary. Drawing upon interviews with funders, founders, and workers associated with well-capitalized (greater than \$100M capital raised) US-based VFs, combined with media analysis of a large corpus including promotional materials, strategic plans, and regulatory filings, this paper explores narrative, technoscientific, and material roots of landless agricultural aspirations. It considers their entanglements with more general aspirations to de-materialize or de-couple as a way to delay, divert, or defeat global environmental catastrophe.

Agro-food futurism and the doxa of efficiency *Julie Guthman, University of California, Santa Cruz*

A 2020 report published by the think tank RethinkX boldly describes a future in which food will be engineered by scientists at a molecular or cellular level and fermented in bioreactors. Producing food this way, the report asserts, will be immensely cheaper as well as environmentally benign, both stemming from a promise of multifold increases in efficiency. While there are many reasons to disrupt contemporary food production, lack of efficiency is arguably not one of them, food production having long been undergirded by logics of efficiency whose consequences have not been benign. And yet, efficiency has become one of the primary promises of not only the alternative protein space which this report promotes, but in a whole host of current prognostications of optimal food futures that can be gained through novel technologies. Based on both text and field-based research on Silicon Valley's recent foray into food and agriculture, this paper will illustrate the multiple domains in which efficiency arguments underpin emerging technologies. It will argue that the doxa of efficiency, operating as a proxy for environmental beneficence, is a product of both the imperative for ag-food tech entrepreneurs to demonstrate morality-infused impact and the limits of what technology-driven innovation can actually offer to agriculture and food.

Interrogating the Mythologies of Ag-Tech: Will the "Digital Agriculture Revolution" Feed Our Planet Sustainably? *Sarah Marquis, University of Guelph*

Proponents of precision agriculture, and the subsequent datafication of farming, frame it as an optimization of the food production process, and thus a solution to an unsustainable food system. This research intends to identify how ag-tech start-ups in Canada embody and perpetuate these techno-solutionist ideologies. By juxtaposing the goals of these start-ups with the desires and needs of farmers in Canada, I will identify the tensions present in the process of digitization and datafication in Canadian crop agriculture. This work will also interrogate whether or not socio-technical systems built upon the imperative of agricultural Big Data collection are enabling or disabling environmental sustainability in the Canadian agricultural landscape. Though the full promise of agricultural Big Data is usually conceptualized as something that will happen in the future, it is still important to question the current ways in which ideologies and worlds are being built through ag-tech now, and how the ag-tech economic ecosystem is driving this process. This paper will compare content from corporate ag-tech websites and marketing materials with the perspectives of Canadian crop farmers and precision agriculture stakeholders. A goal of this research is to demonstrate ways in which ag-tech works to oversimplify complicated processes, relationships, and concerns related to the digitization and automation of agriculture. This work will contribute to scholarship on sociotechnical imaginaries by tracing these stories as they move from corporate spaces to the farm.

Session Organizer:

Karly Burch, University of Otago

Discussant:

Kelly Bronson, Department Of Sociology And Anthropology, University Of Ottawa

373. Load-Bearing Bodies: Unjust Relations and Liberatory Horizons – II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This is the second session in a panel that centers decolonial, feminist science studies to explore material bodies as infrastructures that alternately stabilize and contest structural inequity. It does so by foregrounding the construction of load-bearing bodies—human and otherwise—suspended amidst the tension of unequal relations. These sessions will investigate the

blurred boundaries of bodies and the structures they entail, especially those of racial capitalism and cisheteropatriarchy. Material burdens settle into bodies, embedding privilege and subjection within capacities and orientations that can be difficult to dislodge. At the same time, attuning to bodily matters can bring alternative possibilities into alignment. In this second session, we will explore how minority ethnicity stem cell donation campaigners in the UK encounter individuated care systems that occlude complex realities of racist inequities. Toxic soils in the US south reveal how the violence of chattel slavery and indigenous removal inhabit the allegedly post-plantation present. US imperial designs in Iraq were secured through ‘war on terror’ propaganda depicting the country’s female scientists as bioterrorist femmes fatales. Meanwhile, US regulatory efforts for lead exposure enable environmental racism by attuning primarily to the bodily experiences of white, male, health-insured, industrial workers. Palestinian women leverage fertility treatment to navigate the simultaneity of settler colonisation and climate collapse. By thinking across these papers and others, spread through multiple sessions, we will explore how bodies become scalar archives for uneven intra-actions among techno-political, scientific, and ecological processes. We will address how bodily burdens maintain disparate conditions, and how bodily stuff can animate good relations for liberatory horizons.

Participants:

Whose Load To Bear?: Racially Minoritised Stem Cell Campaigners And The Individuated Fight For Equity *Ros Williams, The University of Sheffield*

Who carries the burden in the drive for health equity? Healthcare institutions? Policymakers? Those experiencing the effects of that inequity? Bone marrow stem cell transplant, a well-established blood disorder treatment, offers insights here. Whilst many people find a match on donor registries, others don’t. Often, it is minority ethnicity patients who end up without donors. In the UK and beyond, such individuals increasingly use social/traditional media to encourage people to register as stem cell donors. They aim to locate their own donor, whilst also diversifying the stem cell registries for future minoritised patients, demonstrating – as Ruha Benjamin notes – how individual and collective care is entangled. Here, I centre the ambivalence of this caring work, undertaken by some of the most vulnerable amongst us. Such campaigners expose their personal illness narratives to unknown publics with the hope of ameliorating the health inequity experienced by many minoritised people who need, but cannot access, life-extending treatment. Via analysis of interviews with campaigners and related social/traditional media data collected for a Wellcome Trust Fellowship, I explore the costs of carrying this burden for an unknown and expansive racialised public – from a loss of privacy to the exacerbation of illness. I argue for the importance of surfacing the vital work these individuals undertake on behalf of themselves and others, and question why those who bear the load to contest structural inequity are often the very people most affected by that inequity, and most in need of respite from the burden to fight it.

Soil, A Black Archive (of Living) *Marisa Solomon, Barnard College, Columbia University*

Toxicity is an ongoing consequence of chattel slavery, indigenous removal and the lines of violence the plantation drew in the soil. Across southern towns, like those that make up Cancer Alley, the economic interests of what Clyde Woods called “the plantation bloc” foreclose the conditions in which the subjugated are supposed to live (or die). Yet, even as toxicity sediments into the landscaped, embodied and spatial wounds cleaved by regimes of violence, it simultaneously produces a colonial archive. The afterlife of the plantation links scales of injury from the body, to the town to the region and beyond. Thus, how does one attune oneself to history’s haunting of all Black towns, particularly in the South, when there is no “evidence” of injury? This talk focuses on Suffolk, Virginia, a small Black post-industrial southern town whose soil is seething with toxicity.

By turning our attention to the exhausted soils of the post-plantation South, I ask where and how histories of violence are made material.

Militarism and Criminalization in Science: Bioweapons, Orientalism, and the War on Terror *Gwen D’Arcangelis, Skidmore College*

My talk highlights the war on terror’s oppression of marginalized peoples in the biosciences. The U.S. invasion and subsequent occupation of Iraq led to the two-and-a-half year detention of two of Iraq’s top scientists—Dr. Rihab Taha and Dr. Huda Ammash—in connection with bioweapons. While the U.S. government never brought formal charges against them, U.S. news media largely vilified them through gendered Orientalist depictions (as wild and uncivilized, or as devious femme fatales). U.S. criminalization of the scientists was yet another node in the war’s destruction of Iraqi society, specifically the nation’s scientific enterprise. At the same time, the U.S. expanded its own bioweapons capabilities, with legislation (e.g., the PATRIOT Act of 2001) allocating more funding to high-level research on germs with potential bioweapons applications. This legislation further reproduced social marginalization in the biosciences through requiring security measures for high-level germ research—including research with non-military applications—that barred access to entire categories of people deemed potential bioterrorists (e.g., those with national origin to countries designated “state sponsors of terrorism” and those with prior criminal records). These security measures, as with the previous example, reinforce a narrative of the trustworthy scientist against a backdrop of bioterrorist Others to be excluded from scientific engagement. Such a narrative perpetuates the ongoing exclusion of oppressed groups—and even entire nations—from full scientific engagement. I illuminate these entanglements of science with U.S. militarism and social hierarchy to open up conversations about how to better direct science to social justice and good relations.

Regulatory bodies: Lead and the industrial whitening of domestic protection *Nicholas L Caverly, University Of Massachusetts Amherst*

The consequences of consuming lead are well understood. Rashes, pain, tremors, developmental disorders, death, and other harms of have been known for decades. Even centuries. Despite successful campaigns to remove lead from consumer products, lead components remain integral within most dwellings in the United States. Regulations claiming to produce lead-free homes are also notoriously drafty. Hundreds of thousands of people experience lead poisoning every year through the material environments in which they live. People of color, especially Black people, are most likely to be lead poisoned. Scholars and activists have seized on this glaring case of environmental racism to note how corporate interests inhibit the operations of regulatory institutions. This paper does not dispute their arguments. And yet, by way of the evidence presented as part of disputes over lead regulations, it also calls attention to how the antiblackness of existing regulations is not merely the product of the (in)actions of technocratic bodies. Racist outcomes are conditioned by the physical, human bodies entailed in the regulatory process. To show this, I track how arguments for (and against) stronger domestic lead regulations rely on occupational lead exposure studies. Their evidence is attuned to adults who are almost always white, men, laboring, unionized, and health-insured. As privileged experiences structure regulatory (in)action, they demonstrate how the racist absence of protection does not simply index compromised institutions. Rather, it also results from the placement of whitened and otherwise protected bodies—rather than others—at the center of regulatory concern.

Making Kin and Making Population: Towards Reproductive Futurity on a Planetary Scale *Gala Antea Rexer, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*

A common argument presented as a way out of the looming environmental catastrophe locates the problem on a demographic scale: people should have less children. Neo-malthusian approaches of overpopulation surface as answers to the current planetary state, despite efforts to trace their racist, colonial, and eugenic histories and entanglements. These anti-natalist perspectives undermine the reality of marginalized communities, for whom reproduction can represent real forms of resistance against the (settler) state and its biopolitical logic of population management. In this paper, I discuss reproductive futurity from the vantage point of those bodies whose birth is always already excluded from national(ist) imaginaries, by turning to the current Israeli-Palestinian situation and the ways in which it structures access to sexual and reproductive health and rights for Palestinian women (citizens of Israel, residents of East Jerusalem, and West Bankers). Drawing from 24 months of ethnographic research with Palestinian women undergoing fertility treatment in Israeli hospitals and interviews with Palestinian health care providers, social workers, and policy makers, I suggest a framework of reproductive futurity that places reproductive justice for marginalized women in a transnational conversation about questions of the Anthropocene. I take the Israeli-Palestinian context as a starting point to think about bodies, populations, and reproduction on a planetary scale, while analyzing current structures of oppression, such as settler colonialism and racial biocapitalism. In so doing, this paper contributes to theoretical and methodological questions relevant to STS, by rethinking reproduction, kin-work, and technology in relational, redistributive, future-oriented ways.

Session Organizer:

Nicholas L Caverly, University Of Massachusetts Amherst

374. Innovation and Inequality in Health and Medicine - III

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

This session investigates how experimental medicine, novel therapeutics, emerging medical technologies, and new diagnostics shape, maintain, and connect to social inequalities. The session addresses how race, gender, class, and other forms of social stratification impact access to and the development of innovative medicine. We are interested in who receives new therapeutics, to which problems or conditions medical attention and innovation attend, and the role of trials and experimentation. Papers might address questions such as: Who stands to benefit from emerging medicine? Who can access new therapies once they are commodified? How are funds and attention applied to - or withheld from - different types of disease? How does medicine drive or reproduce social inequalities? How are vulnerable people or bodies selected as test subjects for emerging therapeutics? We also invite papers that engage with the conference theme and address instances of good (or better) relations among researchers, participants, therapeutics, and illness communities. Here, we seek to consider if and how medical innovations respond to social inequalities, and if we can imagine a more equitable and just approach to experimental medicine. We welcome papers that tie STS research and theory to these concerns and are interested in a broad range of topics and approaches that address tensions between innovation and inequality.

Participants:

A Digital Ethnographic Study of a Technological Fix: Using Telecare to Access Medication for Opioid Use Disorder
Christopher Patrick Caulfield, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Amplified by the material and emotional burdens of the COVID-19 pandemic, the opioid crisis has imposed increasing human costs of lives lost, emotional trauma for families and communities, and financial burdens on healthcare and social systems, with overdose deaths spiking by 20- 50% in counties across the US, year-over-year (Alter & Yeager, 2020). Healthcare by phone or internet, telecare, has been catapulted to a place of prominence in medicine as the standard of care for treatment of drug addiction (Knopf, 2020). This study asks, how

has telecare affecting people who seek treatment for opioid use disorder (OUD)? This paper presents preliminary and ongoing digital ethnographic research of online support groups for opioid addiction and treatment. Preliminary findings of this digital ethnography show how the social stigma associated with drug use is (re)produced in telecare and imbricated within what I term the US juridical-administrative-therapeutic in/justice system despite decades of efforts to reduce stigmatizing attitudes amongst healthcare providers and staff (Association, 2015). Secondly, preliminary findings trace a resistance strategy of those seeking treatment who are subjected to surveillance by video chat with healthcare providers, showing how patients collaboratively find workarounds to exert their agency and defeat systems of surveillance, systems that have been shown to be deeply problematic and contrary to proven harm reduction approaches of meeting people where they are at (Campbell, 2006), underscoring calls for an end to the war on drugs.

Inequalities and Discrimination in Automatic Pain Detection

Wulf Loh, University of Tuebingen; *Alberto Romele*, University of Tuebingen

Individual pain experiences are not only dependent on subjective dispositions and cultural variations, but also on socioeconomic factors as well as implicit biases in diagnostics and care (Anderson et al. 2009; Polshuck et al. 2008). This has serious repercussions for recent research and developments in automatic pain detection and classification, as the AI systems that used to detect and classify individual pain episodes, have to be trained on annotated data that retains the conventional biases. Instead of ameliorating these inequalities, these AI systems potentially “compound” historical injustices (Hellman 2018) with regard to pain detection and treatment. In this case, they can be said to wrongly discriminate against groups already disadvantaged by conventional diagnostics and care. In this paper, we examine and evaluate this danger from the perspective of an automatic pain detection research project (LOUISA; German federal ministry of science). Our research is based on a series of qualitative interviews with the different members of the project, as well as on the ethnographic observation and the active participation in its development. Our ultimate goal is to expanding the existing literature on discrimination in pain detection with a perspective inspired by the STS. Anderson et al (2009) Racial and ethnic disparities in pain. *J. Pain* 10, 1187–1204. Hellman, D. (2018): Indirect Discrimination and the Duty to Avoid Compounding Injustice. In Collins, Khaitan (Eds.): Foundations of indirect discrimination law. Oxford, pp. 105–122. Polshuck, E. L. & Green, C. R. Socioeconomic disadvantage and pain. *Pain* 136, 235–238 (2008).

Orphan Drugs in the City: Clashing Biotechnological Futures At Genzyme’s Boston Plant *Robin Wolfe Scheffler*, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

In 1991, Genzyme selected Boston’s economically-depressed Allston neighborhood as the site of its new biomanufacturing facility. This factory would be dedicated to the production of the firm’s signature product, Ceredase, a treatment for a rare genetic disorder called Gaucher’s disease. This paper uses the urban history of Genzyme’s Boston plant, “A Cathedral of Biotechnology,” as a means of bringing conflicting social imaginaries of biotechnological innovation into conversation. On one hand, Ceredase was the manifestation of a longstanding biomedical promise that grasping disease at its biological roots would produce cures. Moreover, Ceredase and other therapies that Genzyme promised would follow were firmly enmeshed in the political economy of rare disease research, especially the promise that entrepreneurial biotechnology would translate research from bench to bedside. Finally, in seeking subsidies from local governments for the construction and operation of its factory, Genzyme and its allies promised a new postindustrial future for Boston, in which the growth of biomanufacturing would ameliorate the loss of traditional industries. On the other

hand, critics noted that Ceredase was the most expensive drug yet released, drawing attention to the inaccessibility of biotechnology's innovations as well as the need to focus on rare diseases when so many other looming health problems were unaddressed. Debates over the choice of Genzyme's site also revealed the disconnect between the public subsidies sought by the company and the benefits that the neighborhood would receive. Exploring how these views converged on the factory speaks to the intertwined nature of space, science, and social inequality.

Smart Healthcare Systems and Social In-/Justice *Cordula Kropp, University of Stuttgart; Karolin Tampe-Mai, University of Stuttgart*

AI-based health technologies emerge from stochastic analyses of big health data (insurance status, medical record, lifestyle data) and are based on the algorithmic processing of these data, which simultaneously can be turned into assets on global health markets (Birch et al. 2020; Vezyridis/ Timmons 2021). We ask to what extent health equity is affected by algorithm-based services. In addition to data-based bias against subgroups, unequal representation and lack of explicability and validation of AI-based intelligent decision-support systems, vertical disparities in health care (access to, utilization, and quality of services) have consequences for potential discrimination. Health disparities particularly affect people of low socioeconomic status, and the elderly, groups that are more likely to have health-risking lifestyles and higher risks of disease and mortality. Studies from STS draw our attention to both, the risks of algorithmic decision making and the embedding of AI in global health markets (Beer 2017; Fourcade & Johns 2020; Lupton 2017; Mackenzie 2005 Martin 2015). We discuss the promises of AI-based health technologies and its implications into the existing German care system. Our findings from a literature review and expert interviews support assumptions about shifts in key differentiations (health-disease, prevention-therapy, physician-medical informatics, care-product), a fundamental redefinition of concepts of health care, and point to problems of interoperability between different technologies and providers. These challenges are discussed against the goal of health equity for all, esp. sensitive subgroups. First contours of necessary debates on social inequality and AI medicine are outlined.

Session Organizer:

Dagoberto Cortez, The University of Texas at Austin

Chair:

Michael Halpin, Dalhousie University

375. Measurement and Commensuration in Professions, Session II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Quantification and commensuration have been major areas of inquiry in STS in recent years. STS work has highlighted the challenges of measuring the attributes or performance of individuals and of ensuring these measurements are comparable. While regulation and control through tracking has long been a feature of low-wage work, these new forms of quantification and commensuration are increasingly prevalent in high-status professional groups like physicians and nurses. Such forms of quantification and commensuration are often aimed at increasing productivity, agility, and well-being among professionals and occupational workers. They can also be used to assess, quantify and compare knowledge, skills, personal attributes, and emotional states, with the hope that developing measurements and quantifications will offer an alternative to traditional forms of evaluation, and that this might reduce bias in skill assessments. In this session we seek to explore how quantification and commensuration are remaking professional groups and identities, and how new quantification technologies may play a role in professionalizing projects.

Participants:

Conceptualizing the Digitalization of Healthcare Work: A Metaphor-Based Critical Interpretive Synthesis *Chiara Carboni, Erasmus University Rotterdam; Rik Wehrens, Erasmus University; Antoinette De Bont, Erasmus University; Romke van der Veen, Erasmus University Rotterdam*

The digitalization of healthcare work has gained center stage in academic debates spanning disciplines as diverse as medicine, sociology and STS. However, the different analytical interests and methodological traditions of these three strains of scholarship have resulted in quite diverging approaches to this issue. Points of interest have ranged from the (disattended) promise of increased efficiency of healthcare work, to dynamics of (re-)professionalization and (re-)distribution of invisible work, to the disruption of informal organization and connected emotional consequences. In this presentation we foreground the potentiality for theory-making on the digitalization of healthcare work inherent to the systematic cross-contamination of different disciplinary perspectives and related empirical findings. We have performed a Critical Interpretive Synthesis (CIS) centering the ways the digitalization of healthcare work has been investigated in recent STS, sociological and medical literature. To open up assumptions and insights intrinsic to each body of literature for scholars and practitioners in other fields, we propose a metaphor-based variation on CIS approaches. We probe, in turn, what slime molds can teach us about STS's focus on interconnections and materiality, which lessons river engineering offers concerning medical scholarship's discussion of efficiency and proper healthcare work, and how we can better understand sociological analyses of invisible work exploring them through theatrical performances. Thinking through these metaphors, we endeavor not only to make tangible the insights provided by each body of literature, but also to synthesize them in a framework that enables the systematic cross-contamination of different disciplinary perspectives on the digitization of healthcare work.

Quantifying Dutch Nursing Work as an Emancipatory Project *Martijn Felder, Erasmus School of Health Policy and Management; Syb Kuijper, Erasmus School of Health Policy & Management; Roland Bal, Erasmus University Rotterdam; Iris Wallenburg, institute for Health Policy and Management*

We currently witness an expansion of the use of metrics in worlds that are typified as 'soft' and 'affectionate' rather than 'cold' and 'calculative' (Bowker and Star 2000; McKenna 2004). The Dutch (re)organization and (re)valuation of nursing is exemplary. Here, nurse leaders have introduced a toolbox to measure the relationship between a) differentiating between vocationally and bachelor-trained nurses; and b) healthcare outcomes. To do so, the toolbox pursues to quantify both the technical and tacit work that these different 'types of nurses' do beside the bed and beyond. Those that push for role differentiation argue that bachelor-trained nurses can help to strengthen the evidence base of nursing (Watkins 2011) and the translational work that nurses do within healthcare organizations (Allen 2018). As such, nurse differentiation would strengthen the position of nurses vis-a-vis 'nursing others' and contribute to higher quality, responsive and affordable healthcare. The toolbox aims to make these promises tangible, measurable, governable. We ethnographically study how the toolbox interacts with the differentiated nursing practice(s) it intends to make visible and turn into objects of valuation and regulation. We do so by tracing how it is constructed and adapted whilst being implemented within hospitals and by the nursing association. We demonstrate how the toolbox helps to build a 'statistical community' of 'better (trained) nurses' that transcends the boundaries of wards and hospitals; particularly so by (re)articulating – and delimiting – which aspects of nursing can be made visible, comparable and thus be considered 'good nursing work' (Mennicken and Espeland 2019).

Seeking Autonomy to Enact Changes in Care: Organizational Support, Race, and Nurse Autonomy *Katherine Castro Tuangco, Rutgers University New Brunswick*

Scholarship in sociology has focused on an individual's knowledge as one of the main predictors of autonomy in professionals, yet organizational factors may also play a role in predicting autonomy in the workplace. Such organizational factors include the commensuration and quantification of performance in the form of feedback from upper management. Using data from The Newly Licensed Registered Nurse (NLRN) Survey Series, I conduct a series of binary logistic regression models focusing on how well nurses' perceptions of their own knowledge, feedback received from upper management, hospital magnet status, and race predict autonomy for NLRNs working in US hospitals. Nurses who receive feedback more often and work in a magnet hospital have higher levels of self-reported autonomy. White nurses are more likely than non-white nurses to report that they have autonomy to enact changes in the hospital's structure of patient care. I argue that organizational support is important for nurse autonomy and is especially important for non-white nurses who are less likely to perceive they are supported by their organization to enact changes to patient care. This paper contributes to STS scholarship in healthcare and health professions, commensuration, and race.

The use of digital metrics to prove value: the case of the communications professional *Ms M. Valeria Ramirez, Universite Gustave Eiffel - LISIS - CONACYT*

Virtually every communications activity can be tracked and transformed into numbers such as tweets, likes, seconds of video viewed, time spent on a website, newsletters opened as well as the actions resulting from it. Despite all this data, digital metrics seems not to be enough to evaluate content and assess quality. Indeed, the communications professional (corporate, digital, public relations...) struggles to find the right KPI's to assess the efficacy of their actions and prove their impact. To reduce the activity to numbers decorrelates the data from the complexity of the context and choices (Desrosières, 2013; Porter, 1996), but on the other hand, not quantifying their efforts in an "everything is measurable" era puts them into a risk of lacking visibility (Lemieux, 2008) and of being invisible to their peers, target and the management. This metrics related approach turns out to be increasingly problematic when trying to legitimize their role into an organization. This "if it's not measured it doesn't exist" philosophy strikes into an immature profession which was already unconfident in its practices (Watson, 2012) but at the same time internet tracking tools and digitalized measuring instrument offers them an opportunity to professionalize the practice. Thanks to the ethnographic work realised in a communications department and the exploration of industry documents and events; this work shows three main postures adopted face to measurement: utilitarian, anxious, strategic and the different ways in which quantitative measurement has impacted internal conventions and restitution spaces.

Quantification in pharmacist care practices: Managing polypharmacy and the Quantified Self. *Jenny Epstein*

Digitalized health data and polypharmacy is changing the professional roles of pharmacists. As the number of medications used to manage chronic conditions has increased, so has the need to more closely monitor their use. As a result, over the past decade especially, the role of pharmacists in clinical practice is shifting from dispensing medications to monitoring their use to treat chronic diseases. Working under collaborative practice agreements, pharmacists provide direct care managing insulin dosing, anti-coagulants and heart failure medications, among others. As an ancillary medical profession, pharmacists are a cost-effective way to provide routine but time-consuming care to monitor chronic conditions and medications. Using auto-ethnography, clinical observation and professional literature

reviews, I examine these new roles in pharmacist-managed type-2 diabetes clinics. Quantified data will not be examined to measure pharmacists' performance. Instead, I examine how pharmacists access and use digital data from EHRs and home health devices to make decisions about medications. I also examine how this data is used to mediate the use of numbers into daily self-care practices of people living with type-2 diabetes. Ostensibly, in this new iteration as "medication experts," pharmacists work to help patients become self-sufficient managers of the chronic conditions they live with. Frequently however, patients become more reliant on pharmacists for monitoring and measuring and less sure of their abilities as an independent quantified self. Connecting polypharmacy and the use of digital data with emerging professional roles helps elucidate new ways quantification emerges in everyday life.

Session Organizer:

Alexandra Vinson, University of Michigan

Chair:

Kelly Underman, Drexel University

376. Critical Information Studies: A Roundtable on Sociotechnical Theories, Digital Objects and Institutional Practices

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Critical information studies (CIS) is an empirical, political, and educational project. This CIS roundtable will unite and expand the field through an interactive fishbowl format. It has three goals. First, we will ground recent critical investigations of big data, algorithms, and misinformation in decades of research in library and information science. Second, we will discuss the evolution of iSchools as sociotechnical objects shaping these research problems. Finally, we will make space for the burgeoning cohort of STS scholars working in iSchools. In this way we will create a community for CIS within 4S, and support each other's CIS work in our own institutions. For CIS, information is not natural, but constructed. We will discuss the common ties between research that addresses, for example, labor in information systems and the information ideologies that construct 'users.' CIS seeks to remake the power relations produced by and through information. Our roundtable will discuss the political possibilities of our work, how we can, for example, engage in anti-racist and anti-colonial struggles to preserve those institutional records that can support reparations and erase those records that serve as tethers of the carceral state. Finally, CIS rethinks library and information science pedagogy. Our roundtable will discuss how to move iSchool education beyond training interchangeable information professionals who optimize access to information resources, and how to incorporate more critical dispositions from STS. In a moment of institutional ferment, we hope to build models for creativity beyond entrepreneurialism, for abolition over inclusion, and for an information ethics that does not formalize power but redistributes it.

Presenters:

Patricia Garcia, School of Information, University of Michigan

Ryan Shaw, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Tonia Sutherland, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa

Marika Cifor, The Information School, University of Washington

Patrick Keilty, University of Toronto

Session Organizer:

Daniel Greene, University of Maryland

Chair:

Britt Paris, Rutgers University, School of Communication and Information

377. Optical Media: The Impact of Visual Technologies - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Optical media, borrowed from Friedrich Kittler, is an expanded concept that connects photography, film and television with other techniques and

technologies that mediate optics and vision (e.g. microscopes, telescopes, oscilloscopes, echocardiography, ad inf.). Normalized, expected and often desired, optical media shape how we perceive the reality that surrounds us, mediating our understanding and experience of our inter- and intra-relationships with ourselves, others, objects, and worlds. In so doing, they constitute power relationships that reify inequalities and uncertainties, the key themes of 4S 2021, rendering certain people, places, and things visible, invisible, or hypervisible. These issues have grown in importance in the wake of COVID-19 and social distancing, where optical media have become ubiquitous. This panel welcomes interdisciplinary research from STS and neighbouring fields that critically examine the role of these embedded and disruptive technologies in guiding our world views and relationships. By paying attention to the modes of seeing and looking that shape our perceptions, behaviours, and practices we can begin to better address their effects on other information systems including but not limited to the ones we work in, socialize in, and reside in. Questions we ask include how are modes of looking shaped by digital optical media? What potentials are there for visual manipulation, exploitation, or psychological vulnerabilities? What new possibilities for ways of thinking, interacting or organizing information do these technologies offer? Who and what is being rendered visible, invisible, or hypervisible and the power politics of optical media?

Participants:

Surveilling Spectatorship: Smart TV Parental Controls and the Dynamics of Domestic Privacy *Cara Nash Dickason, Northwestern University*

This paper asks what happens to the relational dynamics of domestic life when spectatorship and surveillance converge in Smart TV technologies. Employing a media studies and feminist STS approach, it focuses on the forms of “parental control” sold to consumers as a way to secure the boundaries--and traditional gendered power dynamics--of the nuclear family. “Parental control” operates at the level of visually monitoring what children do, and algorithmically monitoring what children see. These imbricated modes of watching simultaneously invite the gaze of corporations engaging in consumer surveillance, both visual and algorithmic, into the home. I first consider how television viewership integrates with visual surveillance of the home. For instance, an advertisement for Smart Home technologies features parents whose leisurely TV viewing is visually interrupted by the video feed from their front door camera. As their daughter arrives home with her date, they activate the porch light to prevent a goodbye kiss. These optical forms of parental control explicitly monitor what children do, with an eye toward policing gender normativity. Similarly, parental controls directed toward what children watch are marketed through a gendered discourse of “media effects;” the assumption of “child see, child do” often circulates around fears of girls’ exposure to sexual content producing sexual behavior. Surveillance, both parental and corporate, is thus enlisted to enforce a traditional form of domestic privacy based in the invisibility of young women’s sexuality. Multiple modes of looking converge in Smart TV technologies, rewriting the meaning of privacy in the name of normativity.

The Digital Closet: Heteronormativity in Image Recognition and Content Moderation Algorithms *Alexander Monea, George Mason University*

This article analyzes Google SafeSearch’s use of machine vision to automate censorship. First I provide a history of SafeSearch, followed by an overview of Google’s machine vision system and the datasets it is built atop. Next I examine its political implications from five perspectives. First, I demonstrate how English-language semantic biases about sexuality are embedded in WordNet’s ontology. Second, I outline how ImageNet embeds the biases of both image makers and labelers and examine the possibility for automatically outing ‘closeted’ LGBTQIA+ people. Third, I look at instances where explicitness is blurry, focusing on Google understanding the term ‘bisexuality’ as

indicative of pornography. And lastly, I analyze the post-2012, always-on SafeSearch model that requires explicit keywords to trigger pornographic results, which reifies mainstream heteroporn’s dominance online. In closing, I suggest some tactics of resistance.

A Dystopian China Imagined: Rhetorics and Practices in the Resistance of Surveillance Technologies in Detroit *Yuchen Chen; Alex Jiahong Lu, University of Michigan; Jonathan Riley, University of Michigan*

This paper attends to the (shifting) imaginaries and positioning of China embedded in the technological innovation, practices, and resistance in the U.S. We look at how anti-China sentiment is produced through discourse surrounding surveillance technologies, especially facial recognition, which frames China as a dystopian future to avoid. This dystopian future is tied to Cold War imaginaries of China’s oppressive state control over its citizens, a threat that leaders of the U.S. have portrayed in opposition to liberal freedoms and democracy. Our case study focuses on Project Green Light—a city-wide policing surveillance system developed by Detroit Police Department—and its facial recognition capabilities, to explore 1) how activists and citizens against such a system construct China as a dystopian future of total state control to avoid for Detroit; 2) how histories and rhetorics of the Othering of China in the U.S. shape and are shaped by resistance to surveillance; 3) what politics and (racial and nationalist) assumptions are behind this Othering and racialization of resisting surveillance and facial recognition technologies. Through the lens of critical race studies and surveillance studies, we offer a critical archival analysis of newspapers, public archives, government documents, and materials from Detroit city council meetings to trace the genealogy of this Othering of China and our fieldwork in Detroit to understand the perceptions on the ground. In doing so, we offer alternative conceptions of the relationship between surveillance, race/racialization, and resistance.

Psychotic Ecologies of Images *M.R. Sauter, University of Maryland, College Park*

At the end of ON PHOTOGRAPHY, Susan Sontag invites the reader to consider the necessity of a conservationist “ecology” of images, in part in order to shield reality itself from the dominating power of photographic images. Today, the ecology of images is healthy, but the counterpoint with reality Sontag imagined has faltered. Photographic images have not flowed into a harmony with reality, but have taken the leading part. Images and the data derived from images, about images, and for images dominate the social, computational, and governance spheres. “Smart” systems for bodies, buildings, homes, and municipalities elevate cameras, sensors, and the data derived from the images and readings they produce to the level of directive coaches, superintendents, or governors, taking programmatic actions or issuing nudges based on data collected. This paper takes as its central case the now-abandoned Sidewalk Toronto smart city proposal. As a privacy protection measure, Sidewalk Toronto had proposed a surveillance and analysis infrastructure wherein images were analyzed within the physical bulk of the collecting camera itself, sensitive images never leaving the camera’s body. Working with the critical writings of Susan Sontag, Friedrich Kittler, Kelly Oliver, Patricia Williams, Levinas, and Hans Jorg Rheinberger, I propose a philosophical framework for understanding a new “psychotic” ecology of images, wherein epistemic activity occurs primarily within and through automated image-based infrastructures. Using Kittler’s understandings of optical media (and the ways Sidewalk’s systems depart from it) and Rheinberger’s “epistemic things,” this paper unpacks the philosophical implications of cameras as analytical, epistemic engines.

Session Organizers:

Paula Sanchez Nunez de Villavicencio, University of Toronto

Alexander Monea, George Mason University

378. Corona Truth Wars: Testing and Contesting Knowledge in a Hyper-Mobile Pandemic - II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic created a global crisis challenging humankind to develop as quickly as possible reliable knowledge about the virus and its devastating effects on our bodies and societies in order to minimize such harms. This situation of great uncertainty and enormous stakes incited a historically unique international knowledge producing effort by institutionalized scientists and research groups. While debate and disagreement exists within these scientific communities, more controversial are the various competing “outside” forms and sources of information on the virus and its mitigation strategies. Some are clear disinformation campaigns or far-fetched conspiracy theories, others are legitimate challenges to the temporary status quo. In the hyper-mobile context of knowledge production during an evolving pandemic, it is often hard to tell the difference. Questions such as ‘what information is reliable?’, ‘which experts should we follow?’, and ‘what (epistemic) authorities are to trust?’, take center stage in public debates. Prevalent clear-cut distinctions between “real” knowledge controversies and “fake” disruptions of scientific progress obscure the fact that the global quest for truthful knowledge about the virus is entangled with various (geo)political dynamics, government policy pressures, media reporting, platform moderation and public understandings of it all. STS scholars are perfectly equipped with concepts, theories and methods to help understand these complex dynamics involving uncertainty, changing insights, and (covert) manipulation. In this panel we invite scholars working on such “corona truth wars”: we welcome both empirical and theoretical studies on the cultures, politics and technologies of today’s corona knowledge contestations.

Participants:

Assuring Scientific Quality in Times of Pandemic: Changes in Formal and Informal Review Practices *Serge P.J.M. Horbach*, Aarhus University

The Covid-19 pandemic affected science communication and the public use of scientific knowledge. Simultaneously, it impacted on the scholarly publication system and journal peer review practices. Studies have shown that medical journals have strongly accelerated their review processes for Covid-19 related content. This has laudably led to faster knowledge dissemination but also raises concerns about the quality of the review process and subsequently the quality of the published content. To address these questions, this study sets out to assess qualitative differences in peer review practices brought about during the pandemic. It assesses open review reports, editorial decision letters, author responses, and open reader comments, in two medical journals, for Covid-19 related articles, articles not related to Covid-19 published during the 2020 pandemic, and articles published before the pandemic. It finds notable diversity between Covid-19 and non-Covid-19 related articles, including fewer requests for additional experiments, more cooperative comments, and alternative suggestions to address too strong claims. In general, the findings suggest that both reviewers and journal editors implicitly and explicitly use different quality criteria to assess Covid-19 related manuscripts. The open reader comments and wider uptake of post-publication review, further raises questions about the role of scholarly journals to monitor and assure the quality of the published record. This talk will discuss these concerns, relating them to a long STS-history of evaluation and publishing studies, suggesting potential future opportunities for scientific quality assurance mechanisms.

Explicating the Transnational Disaster STS COVID-19 Project *Kim Fortun*, University of California Irvine; *Tim Schuetz*, UC Irvine; *Maka Suarez*, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography; *Duygu Kasdogan*, İzmir Katip Çelebi University

The Transnational Disaster STS COVID-19 Project is a

collaborative project to track and analyze COVID-19 as it unfolds around the world. A signature aspect of the project is its conceptualization of the pandemic as a transnational disaster, leveraging insight from critical studies of disaster, transnationalism and STS. The project leverages digital research infrastructure in ways new to the social sciences, connecting researchers-at-a-distance in collaborative analysis and interpretation. The project also has a strong pedagogical component, drawing in and connecting student researchers in different places. We’ll present the project architecture (based on small, interlinked research groups) and in-process work to produce a suite of place-focused COVID-19 case studies designed to counteract deeply entrenched methodological nationalism by thinking through the lens of transnational STS. The case studies foreground ways data infrastructure and capacity in different places is shaping how COVID-19 is understood, programmatically addressed, and challenges liberal constructs of the social contract.

Localizing a Pandemic: COVID-19 Data Dashboards in U.S. Cities *Burcu Baykurt*, University of Massachusetts Amherst

Since the COVID-19 pandemic began in the United States, many cities have been scrambling to track, analyze, and report on local data. As the pandemic amplified the racial disparities in public health, the reliability and legitimacy of producing publicly available data have become of further concern. This project examines the varying ways municipalities have collected, analyzed, and publicized COVID-19 data since April 2020. It investigates the top 30 US municipalities’ online dashboards of COVID-19 data by drawing on content analysis as well as in-depth interviews with public officials. I argue that COVID-19 dashboards in U.S. cities are neither real-time operational instruments nor official sites of fact-making. Cities remediate COVID-19 data they receive from state or county governments through local dashboards to communicate managerial order during a highly uncertain public event. They also use local numbers to legitimate the risk of coronavirus in places where the residents might need more persuading. If they have the socio-technical capacity to offer more data, they expand the purview of dashboards to tracking local welfare assistance programs. Rather than becoming sites of fact-making, intervention, or participation, municipal COVID-19 dashboards often aim to render local governments legible to the public – rather than the other way around.

The Data Political Spectacle: Testing Knowledge and Inoculating Society in a Pandemic Age *Sofie á Rogvi*, Center for Medical Science and Technology Studies, University of Copenhagen; *Klaus Lindgaard Hoeyer*, University Of Copenhagen

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic is a data political spectacle. It is a disease and a global event which can only be documented and assessed with data. Restrictions and interventions are based on data predictions, and their efficacy is measured based on data estimates and comparisons. Globally, the data political spectacles have varied enormously. Some countries have generated and shared few data, others have flooded their publics with real-time updates, info-graphics, heatmaps, and interactive tables. Restrictions have differed. Public support has varied. Everywhere, however, the authorities’ ‘truths’ about the disease and the potential preventive measures have been contested. In some countries by politicians, everywhere by portions of the publics. Denmark lies at the very top on rankings of trust in government’s handling of the disease. In a collaborative project with epidemiologists, and since the beginning of the first lockdown in March 2020, we have followed perceptions and experiences of the Danish public through time series questionnaires and with interviews. In this paper, we explore symmetrically the voices supporting the government approach and those seeing themselves as in opposition. How is epistemic

authority negotiated and what is the role of data in these conflicts? We show how opposition to the official line is permeated by data. We suggest that, perhaps, there is something about data, as a source of knowledge, deserving our attention. Something which cannot be reduced to an epistemic game of getting the calculation right. How do data come to have meaning to us and how does that meaning-making interact with execution of authority?

Session Organizers:

Jaron Harambam, Institute for Media Studies - KU Leuven

Ehler Voss, University of Siegen

Discussant:

Linsey Jane McGoey

379. The Crisis of AI: Towards a New Paradigm (I)

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

Studying the rapid development of AI reveals its contradictory nature as both panacea and agent of chaos. We formulate this duality as a paradigmatic crisis. For Kuhn (1962), paradigms comprise sets of (i) theories and ideas that determine what questions to ask; (ii) tools and techniques to apply when approaching those questions; and (iii) anomalies that remain inexplicable under an established paradigm. Anomalies accumulate until a field launches into crisis—characterized by competing articulations, explicit discontent, and calls for “extraordinary research.” We argue the crisis of AI derives from a reigning paradigm driven by a central question, “Can computers do X?” The dominance of this paradigm has produced a desultory explosion of research in some areas (e.g., computer vision) and impeded promising potentials in others (e.g., drug discovery). To shift the paradigm of AI, we reformulate its central question as, “What are the conditions of possibility for computers to do X?” The AI crisis also expresses myriad other current crises across the globe. When inserted into such crises, AI systems amplify and transform them unevenly and unpredictably. Contributions thus examine AI in two senses—in crisis and expressing crisis. Papers focus on: 1. mechanisms that have enabled AI interventions to aggravate preexisting frictions; 2. conditions of possibility driving such mechanisms along the dimensions of infrastructures (physical, technical, organizational), institutions (social, economic, cultural, regulatory, legal), and information (technoscientific, media, public); 3. the reigning AI paradigm cultivates these conditions; 4. alternative scenarios fostered by changing the paradigm and the attendant conditions.

Participants:

Is Data Colonialism Worth Fighting? *Iris Bull, Indiana University - Bloomington*

While discussed as early as 1980, notions of ‘digital colonialism’ and/or ‘data colonialism’ are of increasing interest within critical discussions of applied artificial intelligence and machine learning. Problematic and harmful applications of facial recognition technology, in particular, are often caricatured as moral challenges that should prompt urgent investigation into ethical consequences of automation. In attending to specific ethical dilemmas related therein, ‘digital colonialism’ and ‘data colonialism’ operate as organizing principles for the evaluation of problematic applications, unsustainable configurations of digital infrastructures, and/or speculatively-designed systems of oppression. With these analytics in hand, policy writers and engineers are theoretically prepared to shape legal protections and technological limitations in the pursuit of better (or less harmful) applications of AI. Following from Isis Giraldo’s formulation of modernity-coloniality as a framework for investigating articulations of colonialism, I will review current discussions of ‘digital’ and ‘data’ colonialism within cross-sections of histories of computing, critical HCI design, and Internet studies. I will compare philosophies and imaginaries of social order and technology that are inherent within this body of literature. In doing so, I intend to demonstrate analytical limitations reflected within certain imaginaries of ‘digital’ and ‘data’ colonialism that encumber studies of de- or anti-colonial

technological alternatives. Without challenging claims about the significance of dismantling surveillance systems and resisting ‘social caching,’ I argue that these popular frameworks fail to locate the contours of coloniality, and so misjudge the location and character of their imagined bogey-men. Works referenced: Giraldo, Isis. (2016). “Coloniality at work: Decolonial critique and the postfeminist regime.” *Feminist Theory* 17(2), pg. 157-173. Couldry, N., & Mejias, U. A. (2020). *The Costs of Connection: How Data Are Colonizing Human Life and Appropriating It for Capitalism*. Stanford University Press

Strengthening “algoactivism”: integrating workers’ perceptions
Aida Ponce Del Castillo, European Trade Union Institute, Brussels

Workplaces are increasingly digital and algorithms are more and more a key ingredient of the working environment. Algorithmic management and digital surveillance practices are increasingly used in companies, in all sectors and across Europe, not just in companies of the so-called platform economy. The COVID crisis and the increase in the number of people who telework have made that reality more visible. The starting points of my presentation are the findings of two European surveys, one conducted with employers (Eurofound 2020), the other with trade unions (ETUC 2020), complemented by interviews of individual workers. The surveys and interviews focused on worker surveillance and the use of algorithmic management. The presentation will focus on workers’ perceptions and how they experience the use of those tools, highlighting (1) the difficulty to raise the topic with management, and (2) their agency regarding the exercise of their rights and how collective action can be initiated. I argue that these two aspects should be part of the socio-technical AI narrative, thus contributing to “algoactivism”, as coined by Kellogg et al 2020, but with an understanding of the concept that suggests an activist/positive approach rather than one based on resistance.

Proportionality – the Missing Principle in AI Ethics
Maksim Karliuk, Sector of Social and Human Sciences, UNESCO

This paper explores a possible solution to certain unresolved problems pertaining to the tensions that are present among principles in various ethical frameworks for AI. Conceptual and procedural divergences in the sets of principles reveal uncertainty as to which ethical principles should be prioritized and how conflicts between them should be resolved, e.g. larger datasets to unbias AI vs privacy, avoiding harm vs accepting some degree of harm, between private interest and public interests. Moreover, there are externalities, in particular for the environment, as major AI methods currently employed are based on processing of ever-increasing amounts of data and computing power, which leads to increasing energy consumption and consequential impact on carbon emission and depletion of resources. This paper suggests the principle of proportionality and a framework of tests of necessity, desirability, and suitability to address some of the underlying issues and to ensure that other societal priorities are well taken into account. It is argued that at least in certain scenarios the perceived tensions can be false dichotomies, as there are AI methods, which allow transcending conflicts between principles. Proportionality presents a set of conditions that must be satisfied to justify usage of this or that AI method, which can be further expanded to justifying using AI systems as such for a particular purpose. It is an evaluation based upon thorough description of the social narrative and those people and interests affected or protected in it.

Populism and Automation Reconsidered
Matthew Lucky, Department of Political Science, Indiana University-Bloomington

In recent years scholars have linked the economic disruptions induced by new automations in the workplace to the global trend towards populist politics. These narratives argue that technologically generated job losses create a standing reserve of

disaffected citizens. Populist politicians, then, are presented with an opportunity to mobilize “the people” who have suffered economic losses in an antagonistic model of politics against “the elites” perceived as agents of their misfortunes (e.g. Big Tech & coastal elites). These explanations suffer from two deficiencies that I address in this paper. First, from a theoretical standpoint, conceptions of populism in common use do not accurately capture the phenomenon. They are correct to note the hostility directed up the socioeconomic hierarchy from “the people” directed at elites. However, what is neglected here is that populism also entails punching downwards at an “anti-people” (e.g. immigrants and racial minorities). Thus, populist politics is as much about hierarchy enhancement as it is about hierarchy attenuation. Second, from an empirical standpoint the present causal narrative linking automation and populism is out of alignment with prevailing scholarship in political science. Simply put, citizens do not tend to alter their political behaviors when they experience job losses as individuals. I argue that there is a causal link here, though it requires accounting for how automation induced job losses interact with group identity and status threat. Overall, I contributed an updated accounting of the connection between automation and populism that corrects for the theoretical and empirical concerns highlighted above.

From Wellness to Fairness: A Participatory Project Approach for Pushing Forward Fair AI *Julian Anslinger, IFZ - Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture Graz, Austria; Christopher Frauenberger, Cooperative Systems Research Group, University of Vienna, Austria; Center for Human-Computer Interac; Michael Funk, Cooperative Systems Research Group, University of Vienna, Austria; Peter Reichl, Cooperative Systems Research Group, University of Vienna, Austria; VRVis Vienna, Austria; Anita Thaler, IFZ - Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture*

In December 2019, the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG invited 30 researchers and practitioners from various fields (who had never seen each other before) to a wellness hotel in order to create innovative project proposals on the topic of fair and trustworthy AI in Austria. What started as an interesting exercise in participatory project design eventually turned into projects like dAlalog.at, which aims at creating new methods of participatory technology design for establishing fair AI. However, already unpacking the notion of “fair AI” with an interdisciplinary team soon revealed itself to be a Pandora’s box as discussed in this contribution. Starting with a critical reflection of the scopes and meanings of the terminology used, we explore the nature of intelligence ascribed to technology as well as the question of who or what can then act fairly. We address the locus of agency, accountability, and responsibility, and discuss the corresponding role of explainability and transparency in AI. Moreover, fairness itself may risk of serving as a red herring, as it reductively suggests that algorithmic bias is the main cause of concern, when most of the injustice brought on by AI is rooted in the identification and modelling of the task itself. Hence, after further clarifying the philosophical conditions of possibility of fairness versus justness and equality, we argue that designing just or desirable AI technology may capture better the concerns of our society and conclude that participating in the design of AI technology is inevitably linked to entering a political arena.

Session Organizer:

Katreen Boustani, Indiana University - Bloomington

Chairs:

Hamid Ekbia

Katreen Boustani, Indiana University - Bloomington

Discussant:

Hamid Ekbia

380. The Material-Semiotics of Global Health Infrastructures I: Afterlives and Repurposings

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

What can be made of built and provisional global health infrastructures? How do we begin to depict and analyse the complex workings and material heterogeneity of sprawling networks of people, evidentiary systems, communication channels, and the mundane and seemingly ‘micro’-interacting components and artefacts that make-up, and are made up by, global health work? This panel thinks with and through the many questions raised by the persistence of global health infrastructures, bringing together case studies that centre their coexistence, adaptability, and fragility to challenge the “modern infrastructure ideal” (Furlong 2014). We suggest that the dispersed relations, affects, and transactions that characterize these sociotechnical systems enact and assign meaning to (racial, sexual, gender) differences that congeal infrastructures. In this, we move beyond viewing difference (e.g., non-heterosexuality or blackness) as merely fraught, socially constructed variable that facilitates interventions into health or behaviour. Instead, we consider how forms of difference are conjured, orchestrated, and sedimented within global health infrastructures. Questions pertinent to our discussions include: How are colonial, racialized, gendered, and other tropes, stereotypes, and assumptions reshuffled and recycled in submerged, non-explicit ways in present-day global health worlds? How do global health infrastructures work—not only through multiple layerings of mutually reinforcing networks—but also, more dissonantly, through less-visible repurposings and co-optations that meet unacknowledged exigencies contradictory to the aims of their original architecture? How do we understand and analyze productions and valuations of deprivation and difference—the vital substrates on which global health infrastructures materialize, animate, flourish, and come undone? References Furlong, Kathryn. 2014. “STS beyond the ‘modern infrastructure ideal’: Extending theory by engaging with infrastructure challenges in the South.” *Technology in Society* 38: 139-147.

Participants:

“But It _Feels_ Colonial”: Knowing and Feeling Empire in Global Health *BETSEY BEHR BRADA, Reed College*

What does colonialism feel like? And would you know it was happening before it was too late? Independently of one another, American and Batswana clinicians pondered a gap between what they thought they knew of US-driven global health and their own experiences: “I know it’s not colonialism,” they mused aloud to me, “but it _feels_ colonial.” This disquietude emerged in conversations in southeastern Botswana’s clinical spaces, where both American and Batswana clinicians engaged in treating HIV-positive patients struggled to assign meaning to their own and one another’s actions and situate them related to spatial, temporal, moral, and geopolitical dimension of global health. From the earliest days of PEPFAR, the expansion of access to antiretroviral treatment across the African continent and the emergence of US-driven public-private partnerships for global health has paralleled the expansion of US military presence in sub-Saharan Africa. But while scholars have pointed out that the logics and logistics behind military and global health interventions are far more intertwined than they first appear (Keller 2006; Nguyen 2009), fewer accounts explore individuals’ efforts to acknowledge this overarching governance of life and death from within spaces so wholly consumed with “making live.” Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork in southeastern Botswana, this paper proceeds from clinicians’ articulated difference between knowing and feeling colonialism to examine the fears and fantasies that make the imperial force of global health both unknowable and intimately perceptible in southeastern Botswana.

Capturing men: Race, value, and the enclosure of (key) populations in Africa *Cal Biruk, McMaster University*

Capture-recapture, a method devised for estimating wildlife population sizes using technologies like bird banding, has been repurposed for use with hard-to-count human ‘key populations,’

including African MSM. Uncomfortable analogies that inhere in counting Africans as if they were animals prompt analysis of how ‘population’—knowledge object and container of saveable lives—is constituted by racialized suspicion, transspecies carcerality, and technologies of enclosure. I present an ethnographically-informed analysis of capture-recapture, interspersing vignettes of wildlife ecology and global health population-projects to gesture at interspecies biopolitical entanglements. After explaining the pertinence and value of quantifying key populations amid the “end of AIDS,” I attend to the social kinetics of counting MSM on-the-ground, examining practices like mapping HIV hotspots, ‘capturing’ HIV+ men, and ‘tagging’ humans with trinkets like hand-mirrors or bracelets. The article excavates submerged racialized ontologies of global health’s metrics, concepts, sociotechnical infrastructures, and technologies, yet to be explicitly addressed in the literature.

Global Health Infrastructures and the “New” Racial Science of Key Populations in HIV Programs *Robert Lorway, University of Manitoba*

This paper examines the work that global health infrastructures perform in making up kinds of people. Following how a set of surveillance techniques for HIV prevention — including geographic hotspot mapping, bio-behavioural assessments, and microbiome and molecular analyses — are increasingly welcomed into a particular health administration sector in Kenya, reveals an emergent regime of measurement that operates as a form of racial science. The surveillance of groups of people who are highly marginalized, stigmatized, and criminalized in Kenya indeed hinges on many of the same pre-occupations as colonial era scientists of race — that is, place, behavior and biology. Borrowing insight from Simone Browne’s “Dark Matters”, however, racial difference is viewed as more than a byproduct or effect of surveillance practices. It is inherent to and deeply ingrained in the techniques and surveillance infrastructures themselves in ways that make race both undetectable and highly pervasive.

Possibilities for Infrastructural Change in Black Maternal Health in the Post-COVID World *Adeola Oni-Orisan, UC San Francisco*

In the time since COVID-19 was declared an international pandemic last year, conventional structures for global health programming have evolved and expanded rapidly to meet the urgent challenge that COVID-19 posed. This paper, based on 12 months of reproductive health clinical practice and community engagement in a neighborhood of San Francisco particularly impacted by COVID-19, asks what do these rapid infrastructural changes prompted by COVID-19, tell us about what has always been possible but never prioritized? How does this new infrastructural responsiveness expose racist underpinnings of certain global health policies and programming? What can we learn about the potential for infrastructural change to respond to the relatively slow, largely preventable crisis of Black maternal death in United States? Working at the intersections of critical race theory, Black feminist health science studies and critical global health, I explore these questions with a particular focus on the innovative work of One Love Black Communities, an organization created shortly after the start of the pandemic to attend to needs of Black birthing people in San Francisco.

Session Organizer:

Cal Biruk, McMaster University

Chair:

Cal Biruk, McMaster University

Discussant:

P. Sean Brotherton, University of Chicago

381. Ways of Healing: Exploring non-Biomedical Cures as Emancipatory and Biopolitical Knowledge-Practices - II: Emancipation, profane cures and bioinequalities in more-than-

biomedical healing

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Participants:

Who Resists? Historicities of Home, AMR and the Cultures of Healing *Maria J Santemas, Consejo Superior de Investigaciones Cientificas*

In the social landscape of infectious diseases, microbe’s activities show the relationship between history and biology (de Chadarevian 2010; Ladecker 2016). Pathologist Mary Barber in London detected the phenomena of antibiotic resistance in the late 1940s. From Barber to the session held at the Spanish Parliament on October 22nd 2018 on bacterial resistances, from which an agreement came in November, a long history of resistances proceeded. While the hospital was regarded as a safe, clean place where patients could be treated and cured, the majority of sick people has healed at home. Home is the main place of healing, the place in which to resist. Home as a concept introduces the gendered dimension of healing and of antibiotic resistances; as did the microbiological laboratory. It is at home where the intestinal flora was preserved – by nurturing, as if a practice for the life of plants - when it was attacked by prescribed antibiotics that contribute to kill a good part of such flora. Inspired in the history of women healers and on my own research on the history of penicillin in Spain, I will reflect on the absence of homes and home care in historical reconstructions. At home, women remain crucial healers from the early days of the invention of hygiene as a health practice. I will try to briefly present a proposal to analyse the present from this view of home as a healing space with epistemological meaning.

Practices of ‘Reversal’ Towards Remediating Diabetes in Urban India *Pallavi Laxmikanth, The University of Adelaide*

Diabetes is ubiquitous in urban India, commonly attributed by biomedicine and public media to poor individual dietary and lifestyle choices (Pathak 2019, Solomon 2016). The chronic nature of the illness and the need for compliance with medicine for proper blood sugar control are the primary institutional rhetorics employed to engage a patient in self-care. This premise of the ‘management’ of blood sugars over a ‘cure’ for diabetes implies a life-long dependency on medicine and medical care. In this paper, I explore, how, through the language and practices of ‘reversal’, people with diabetes in Hyderabad find this mode of care to be incompatible with their understanding of the body and health. Engaging local dietary experts, YouTube based keto diet practitioners, ayurvedic remedies and biomedical technologies, they stop taking medication and change their dietary patterns to ‘reverse’ their diabetes. Beyond the scholarship that commonly identifies this ‘non-compliant’ behaviour as attributable to specific cultural beliefs, I suggest that my participants display ‘good relations’ between multiple medical assemblages. Their practices are not ‘anti-biomedicine’, rather, they privilege the conception of health employed by the assemblage over the explanatory model provided. Their view of ‘health’ as a continuous process of self-improvement that foregrounds the situatedness and relationalities of the body with and within society and ecology, differs from the ‘backward-looking’ reactive approach used by biomedicine to problem-solve (Alter 1999). Consequently, they re-define diabetes not as an illness that should be ‘controlled’ through medication, but as a problem of the ‘body’ and its needs, which requires multiple alternative solutions and care practices (Mol 2010). References • Alter, J. S. (1999) ‘Heaps of health, metaphysical fitness: Ayurveda and the ontology of good health in medical anthropology.’, *Current anthropology*, (February). doi: 10.1086/200060. • Mol, A. (2010) *Care in practice : on tinkering in clinics, homes and farms*. Edited by A. Mol, I. Moser, and J. (Jeannette) Pols. • Pathak, G. (2019) ‘Polycystic ovary syndrome, medical semantics, and the political ecology of health in India’, *Anthropology and Medicine*, 8470.

doi: 10.1080/13648470.2018.1544606. • Solomon, H. (2016) *Metabolic Living: Food, Fat and the Absorption of Illness in India*. Duke University Press. doi: 10.1215/9780822374442.

In Search of a Cure: Chronic Kidney Disease and Migrant Workers in Contemporary China *Xisai Song, Cornell University*

This paper offers an ethnographic study of how migrant workers struggle with chronic kidney disease (CKD) in contemporary China. During my year-long fieldwork in 2019, I found many migrant workers suffering from CKD questioned and avoided biomedical treatments. Instead, they took long journeys to seek remedies of traditional Chinese medicine searching for a cure, despite biomedical doctors telling them that CKD is incurable. This paper focuses on the therapeutic journeys of one middle-aged male construction worker, Jin, as an example. The CKD treatment plan in biomedicine requires regular clinical visits, routine medication, proper exercise and diets, and light use of labor, which Jin found incompatible with a blue-collar worker's lifestyle. In addition, his inability to comply with medical advice made him extremely anxious that his CKD would progress to kidney failure quickly. Kidney failure would deprive his ability to work, which is detrimental to the lives and livelihood of his whole family. Therefore, Jin gave up biomedical treatments soon while traveling across the country instead to visit physicians of traditional Chinese medicine. In this paper, I argue that the regimes of care for CKD in biomedicine are underlain by normative institutional, social, and temporal orders that displace socio-economically underprivileged people in nuanced ways. As a consequence, migrant workers embrace alternative therapeutic attempts to imagine different prognoses and to grasp new possibilities of life.

Peripheral embodiments, cohabitation with microbes and practices of care *Katerina Kolarova, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Tereza Stockelova, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Lukáš Senft, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences*

Recent research suggests dependency between the state of one's microbiota and one's health. Acknowledging the microbes inhabiting the human gut opens new ways to 'doing health' and 'doing care'. Growing out of ethnographic research with people with disabilities (in particular people living with various gut diseases), this paper explores the often ambivalent encounters of humans and microbes to rethink embodiments, subjectivity and 'more-than-human-sociality' (Tsing 2013). We explore how complex subject positionings come to matter across the human/microbe border in health- and life-sustaining practices of people with disabilities, and how the materiality of these cohabitations produces specific "situated biologies" (Niewöhner and Lock 2018). To unpack these questions, we build on feminist disability conceptualisations of "peripheral embodiments" (Mitchel and Snyder 2015) and "leaky bodies" (Shildrick and Price 1998) and examine how the microbial agents may be included in the concepts of porous, unstable, non-unitary embodiments and how the practices of care extend to the care for the microbes. The practices of developing and taking care of one's microbial colonies and networks are both drawing on local and 'traditional' knowledges and current biomedical research, which they variously combine. While the local knowledge of working with microbes (e.g. in food fermentation) is relatively accessible and cheap, the biomedical products may be expensive for many. In this regard, we examine the ways in which probiotic approaches and the microbial agents themselves become commodified on the postsocialist 'health' markets through individualised therapies.

Session Organizer:

Andrea Núñez Casal, University of Oxford, UK

Chair:

Coll de Lima Hutchison, London School of Hygiene and Tropical Medicine

382. Vision Expanded: Using Multimodal Research Designs to Empirically Situate Technologies of Vision

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Participants:

Interfaces: On the Relationality of Race, Face and, Vision. A Multimodal Intervention. *Ildikó Z. Plájás, Leiden University*

This paper problematizes vision in relation to the face, race and affect. It argues that vision is not a neutral or objective technology, offering a direct window into the world and the 'visible' phenotypic variations existing within it. Quite the opposite. Vision is deeply invested in creating these variations itself. I draw on the metaphor of the 'interface' to emphasize that vision emerges 'in between' the eyes, bodies, objects and ideas of belonging and otherness. As such, vision becomes a material and political technology that enacts certain people as racial others. To attend to the materiality and politics of vision, I bring together three stories. In these stories faces are drawn, seen or identified while race hides or surfaces in intriguing ways. Through these stories we learn that race is saturated with affect and is recalled in objects and bodies. In addition, this paper offers a novel methodological approach. It employs the eyes of the reader not only to read but also to watch. Vision itself becomes a technology, this time not to produce or reinforce, but to disturb and perhaps even undo ideas of racial otherness. Experimental montage is used as a 'generous method' to attend to the complexities, incongruities of the stories about faces and race. It does not allow us to settle on a simple/single narrative but forces us to stay close to the multiplicities and messiness of how we see faces (and race) in practice.

Making surveillance tangible: sensorial renderings of algorithmic vision *Francesco Ragazzi, Leiden University; Ildikó Z. Plájás, Leiden University; Ruben van de Ven*

Technologies of surveillance such as facial recognition, but also social media content moderation, lie detection at the border are becoming sensorial: they develop awareness for images, patterns, body temperatures, facial movements. Activists have criticized them for their ethical and legal impact, in particular when it comes to ethnic and racial bias, privacy and fundamental rights. Yet surprisingly, the public's acceptance for them has never been higher. The reason for this disconnect, we suggest, is that computer vision technology, when deployed in the field of surveillance, enacts multiple regimes of visibility which produce risk along particular lines of race, sex, ethnicity, class, etc, while remaining itself invisible. Similarly, it blackboxes the process through which it translates sensorial data – images, movements, sounds, body temperatures – into computable representations, making it further inscrutable and remote. In this paper, we thus ask a simple question: how can we make surveillance, mediated through computer vision, visible and sensorial? How to mobilise the senses not only as the object of our inquiry, as to learn more about the sensorial attunements of algorithmic vision, but also as a method to sensorially engage the social scientific community? Based on an original dataset of actors, institutions, computer vision devices and datasets and the images they produce we propose tactics of visibilization and sensorialization of otherwise hidden acts and practices of surveillance.

Mutual Aesthetic Formations: Collaborating toward Shared Field Visions. Notes from the 'Food Citizens?' Project *Cristina Grasseni, Leiden University; Federico De Musso, Leiden University*

We present the work-in-progress digital platform of the ERC project "Food Citizens? Collective Food Procurement in European Cities. Solidarity and Diversity. Skill and Scale."

Through this mock-up, we reflect on how to share the researchers' visions emerging from independent fieldwork in different sites (Turin, Gdansk, Rotterdam). The focus of our investigation are networks of relations, acknowledging that 'the making of bonds in modern times depends on media and mediation' (Meyer 2009: 6). The researchers used deliberate techniques to critically reflect on their positioning in the field and encourage feedback. The fieldworkers employed cultural mapping, audiovisual documentation, and video-based elicitation techniques, as forms of co-production not only of media but of ethnographic meanings. Co-production represents a space for ethnographic relationality with research collaborators, colleague researchers and potentially our audience. Following Herzfeld's ethnography with apprentice artisans in Crete (2004: 92-3), in the digital platform we select and cross-edit significant sequences regarding comparable skills or processes, but employed in diverse contexts (for example, social gardens in Rotterdam, Turin and Gdańsk). This is particularly relevant when trying to visualize what solidarity and diversity look like in a comparative way, or debates on enskilment and de-skilling, upscaling or scaling out. Audio-recorded events, meetings and activities, rough cuts and edits, or archival and web documentation can thus be 'revisited', either in recorded collective conversations or in individual, semi-structured interviews. Thus digital visual media not only documents but also dynamically represents collective food procurement repertoires as emerging from the field, during longitudinal participant observation at each site.

Plotting Data: Acts of Collection and Omission *Ruben van de Ven*

Datasets are the material through which algorithms for computer vision learn to see the world. Algorithmic models are conditioned to distinguish patterns and make predictions by imitating existing structures in these vast collections of data. But datasets for machine learning are not a distilled version of reality: in their creation, conflict and ambiguity are omitted in favour of turning the world into its computable double. The algorithm will never be exposed to these frictions, it remains blind to them. How do we bring forth narratives that make other interpretations possible? Narratives that let us re-engage with the structures and individuals that are to be folded into the computer model. We will discuss tactics of instilling affective relations back into datasets by presenting a series of three alternative interfaces to canonical datasets for machine learning. These interfaces encourage a re-evaluation about the dominant visualities of data visualisation (eg. Johanna Drucker, 2011). They don't engage with the vastness of the collection by means of statistics, but rather shift the attention to its individual entries. Each interface guides the viewer through the structures and cultures that have been encoded in the collection. As such, they raise attention for the practices of collection and curation that shape the limits of computer vision.

Session Organizer:

Ildikó Z. Plájás, Leiden University

383. Caring Economies I

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

This group of five papers represents the first of three "Caring Economies" sessions. Discussant is Emily Yates-Doerr.

Participants:

A Care Economy: Postpartum Home-Care Helpers in South Korea *Yoonjung Kang, University of Pennsylvania, James Joo-Jin Kim Program in Korean Studies*

Korean culture, echoing broader Asian cultural, ethnomedical conceptions of physical and spiritual vulnerability of postpartum women, has developed distinctive postpartum healthcare beliefs and behaviors, called "traditional Korean postpartum care." Korean women's persistent practices of traditional postpartum

care eventually induced the commercial postpartum care service industry which was largely divided into the residential postpartum care facility service and the postpartum home-care service in South Korea in the mid-1990s. Unlike the postpartum care facility service largely operated by nurses and doctors, the postpartum home-care service is delivered by lay middle-aged women trained by private agencies. As an individual contractor, these postpartum home-care helpers take care of postpartum women and babies in individual homes for two to four weeks. Differentiating themselves from ordinary housekeepers, the postpartum home-care helpers define their roles and responsibility as "professional" postpartum care workers and simultaneously situate themselves as "motherly" carers for the postpartum woman and the newborn baby. This paper examines the creation of the postpartum home-care industry, the qualification processes of the home-care helpers, and the nature of the postpartum home-care work in relation with a gig and care economy. By doing so, the paper engages in the discussion of care, not only an interpersonal morality but also as a driving force that redistributes materials, labor, emotions, and power in the sophisticated capitalist market economy.

Economies of Recognition: Indigenous Midwifery and Feminized Care Labor under Bolivia's Intercultural Health Reforms *Gabriela Morales, Scripps College*

During the presidency of Evo Morales in Bolivia, health policies created new opportunities for practitioners of Indigenous traditional medicine to work in public clinics. Yet traditional healers also had to take on new caring practices as they shifted to working in the clinical context. Institutional actors especially expected parteras (midwives) to take on the feminized care labor of providing "psychological support" for patients during childbirth. Whereas parteras outside the clinical context engaged in a range of tinkering practices that tied the body to home, community, and land, in the clinic their role primarily became that of comforting the patient to facilitate the biomedical doctor's intervention. Moreover, parteras (and other healers) were not compensated for their labor. Based on ethnographic research in a Bolivian highland hospital, this paper grapples with the implications of an economization of care that simultaneously demands new forms of labor and does not compensate them. I foreground continuities with historical processes of devaluing Indigenous caring entanglements with the land under colonial-capitalist constructions of rational, productive labor. Against the backdrop of these deeper histories, Aymara parteras working in the hospital selectively engaged institutional framings by positioning themselves as a warmer alternative to the violence of hospital obstetrics. Yet, by drawing together multiple herbal, massage-based, and biomedical techniques, they also challenged the clinical separation of the body from good relations with wider landed worlds. In attending to these tensions, I suggest that care practices are both shaped by economic regimes of labor and become key sites for contesting them.

Making up survivors: economies of care and Post Intensive Care Syndrome *Angela Ross Perfetti, The University of Pennsylvania*

In this paper, I take up the question of how economies shape the provision of care. Particularly, I want to challenge the notion that diseases exist prior to caring economies. Post Intensive Care Syndrome (PICS) is an emerging illness category that has come to describe an array of symptoms that patients experience after discharge from hospital Intensive Care Units (ICUs). These survivors are known to suffer new or worsening impairment in physical functioning, cognition, and mental health, ranging from memory impairment to muscular weakness and anxiety. Using ethnographic and archival data, I explore how caring economies, from actual financial resources to structures of professionalization, inform the progressive diagnostic formulation of an illness. I demonstrate how standardized health-related quality of life measures, institutionalization of "intensive

care,” increase in intensive care utilization and survival, and a need for material resources to support research and clinical services were folded into a “new disease of medical progress” at multiple levels of discourse. I argue that these economies of care not only structure the parameters by which clinical services are rendered, but actually contribute to the way that the suffering of patients comes to be named and recognized in the first place. The story about ICU survivors and PICS is part of a larger story about how subjectivities emerge within entangled relations of care, power, structures of finance, and economies of affect, and helps to show how these relations unfold at the level of discourse.

Music Therapy and Caring Economies in Hospitals during COVID-19 *Meredith Evans, York University*

Drawing from my anthropological fieldwork with music therapists working in Canadian and American hospitals both before and during the COVID-19 pandemic, this paper asks: how do music therapists navigate competing economies of care in biomedical contexts? Through analyzing an ethnographic description of a hospital music therapy session alongside interviews with music therapists about their clinical work, I demonstrate how music therapists participate in competing clinical caring economies. Through offering what ethnomusicologist Jim Skyes (2018) calls ‘musical gift-giving’ in ordinary music therapy care sessions, I argue that music therapists cultivate gift economies of relational care through moments of musical connection and affective intimacies. I will situate this analysis in a discussion of how music therapists’ gift economies of care are co-produced by the wider neoliberal health care context, drawing on stories of the ways in which music therapists struggle to assert their professional legitimacy, finance their care practices, and frame music therapy as a valuable commodity for hospital institutions. Finally, I explore how the COVID-19 pandemic heightened the visibility of complex moral economies of care in the clinic by illustrating how music therapists navigate the ‘essential’ or ‘nonessential’ character of hospital music therapy in pandemic times.

The Work of Resilience: Intensive Care Medicine, Covid-19, and Spaces of Affective Labor *Harris Solomon; Neelima Navvuluri, Duke University; Charles William Hargett, Duke University; Peter Kussin, Duke University*

Based on a collaborative ethnographic study of healthcare workers in a US hospital intensive care unit, this paper asks: How might pandemic “resilience” be understood as a spatialized problem of work? The COVID-19 pandemic has radically intensified demands for resilience in healthcare work, especially in the spaces of intensive care units (ICUs) which face constant pressure to adapt to surging patient loads, rapidly-changing protocols, and an uneven supply of personal protective equipment. Given the demands of for-profit medicine in the US and the extraordinary stress of the pandemic, promoting what administrators term “a culture of resilience” seems imperative. But what do spaces of resilience look like, and how might they reveal the intimate costs of healthcare under capitalist regimes? Based in feminist STS critiques of labor, the paper focuses on the spatial demands on resilience, through ethnographic cases of (a) the gendered labor of ICU workers that emerges in the isolation space of a Covid-positive patient room; (b) the labor forged across spaces of the carceral state and the vitalist state, as ICU workers care for prisoners during the early phases of the pandemic; and (c) the affective labor demands in a context when the pandemic accelerates the ongoing process of corporatizing academic medicine. Across the cases, we argue for a deeper understanding of the spaces of affective pandemic labor, wherein resilience is not naturalized but itself is a spatial economic form. This can reveal how maintaining “good relations” is often hard-won, and how care economies develop through in localized transformations of work.

Session Organizer:

Martha Lincoln, San Francisco State University

Discussant:

Emily Yates-Doerr

384. Emergent Orders in the Governance, Institutions and Knowledge Economies of Genome Editing Technologies - III

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

In the wake of the rapid development of novel genome editing technologies for manipulating DNA, most notably the CRISPR-Cas9 system, a wide variety of actors are vying for influence and access over their governance, development and use. Scientists, biohackers, patients, regulators, bioethicists, disability justice advocates, venture capitalists, biopharma and agriculture firms, among others, are contributing to and contesting the development of institutions for governing these biotechnologies. Key to these dynamics are the discourses, processes and practices through which existing scientific, social, political, economic and ethical orders are disrupted, co-produced, and stabilized to form emergent orders, and how and why some possibilities are opened while others are constrained. This paper session invites research that examines and explores the intertwined development of genome editing technologies and social institutions from diverse perspectives and contexts, and across different applications (e.g. agriculture; health and biomedicine; environmental management and gene drives). What discourses, processes, practices and norms are important for governing these novel biotechnologies? How is increased access to and expanded use of these biotechnologies reconfiguring existing social and institutional orders, and leading to new ones? How can we imagine and enact more democratic forms of engagement with and governance of novel biotechnologies? Overall, we are interested in developing a comparative and critical picture of the emergence of new social orders as the ability to modify DNA becomes commonplace, and in doing so, identify sites where existing inequalities or asymmetries of power are reproduced and can be addressed.

Participants:

Promissory Ethical Regimes: Publics And Public Goods In Genome Editing For Human Health *Matthias Wienroth, Northumbria University; Jackie Leach Scully, Newcastle University*

Our paper analyses promissory discourse for genome editing and human health in the UK, attending to the articulation of public goods and their beneficiary publics. Focusing on promissory reasoning about an emerging technology field as anticipatory, and ethical considerations as integral to such debates, the notion of ethical regime as a mode of governance is applied to the concept of promissory regime. By analyzing key documents and interviews with opinion leaders — thus focusing on the discursive dimension — an enabling promissory ethical regime for genome editing, and its contestation are identified. This regime posits scientific knowledge production now, and improved treatment or prevention of hereditary diseases later, as key goods of genome editing for human health, and as a sociotechnical project worthy of support. Specific publics are created as beneficiaries. These publics and goods play out as ethical rationales for the promissory governance of the emerging field of human genome editing.

“DNA Of The Country”: Situating Genomic Technologies Within Archival Praxis *Madeleine Mendell*

In 2020, the Australian National Film and Sound Archive (NFSA) completed a pilot project to explore synthetic DNA as a storage solution for audiovisual archives. They chose footage of Aboriginal-Australian athlete Cathy Freeman’s gold medal race at the 2000 Sydney Olympics as the subject. This paper explores the repeated statement by the NFSA - that Freeman’s victory is ‘a part of the DNA of the country’ and thus worthy of storing onto DNA - as a framework for discussing the intersection of metaphor and material within this new storage medium. DNA makes readily apparent that the archive is not a metaphor, that its technological materialities must be taken seriously in order to

contend with the racial and colonial projects that have reappeared as genomics and cultural heritage institutions collide at the site of data storage. In using preservation as a methodology, I explore how archival care and maintenance operate at the cellular and digital levels. Scientific practice produces technologies like synthetic DNA. Scientific practice also produces archives. Building on the work of STS scholars like Kim TallBear, Mél Hogan, and Evelyn Fox Keller, alongside digital preservation and archival scholarship (Clifford Lynch, Jennifer O'Neal), I approach the archive for its material conditions. From the molecule to the bitstream, the introduction of synthetic DNA and by proxy, metaphors of life and control, is poised to reconfigure the archive. I identify the archive as a critical site where issues of race, sovereignty, and nation are negotiated through the institutional power to wield DNA as a technology.

Sexuality and Biodigital Publics *Kate O'Riordan, University of Sussex; Sandra Nelson, University of Sussex, UK*

In 2012, the genetic testing company 23andMe turned its attention explicitly to sexuality research, and most recently, has been involved in large scale studies in this area (Ganna et al., 2019). The company frames this initiative in terms of forging good relations with the public, claiming that it was driven by customer request and that diversity enables better science. While interdisciplinary scholarship has critiqued 23andMe in terms of race (Mittos, Blackburn & De Cristofaro, 2018; Scodari, 2017) and disability rights (De Paor & Blanck, 2016; Schlauderer, 2019), little work has been conducted regarding company's foray into studying sexuality. Addressing this gap, this project seeks to contribute to STS along the following lines of inquiry: Why have consumer genomics companies taken an interest in sexuality research? Why do LGBTQ+ subjects participate in these research initiatives? What are the LGBTQ+ identities and publics that are constructed by genomics? Theoretically, we consider the formation and structure of digital publics and counterpublics (boyd, 2010; O'Riordan, 2013; Warner, 2005), and methodologically, we implement both document analysis and qualitative research. Using 23andMe as an empirical basis, we analyze genomic and sexuality data collection, routing, and storage practices (Annas & Sherman, 2014; Stoeklé et al., 2016). Companies like 23andMe define LGBTQ+ publics through intentional and incidental processes of inclusion and exclusion, interpellate them through their interfaces and data categorization procedures, and regulate them through their policies. We investigate the implications of these studies, considering their limitations and their beneficial and harmful effects on LGBTQ+ publics.

Extra-Institutional Science: Navigating Do-It-Yourself Biology in Great Britain, Germany and Canada *Anna Verena Eireiner, University of Cambridge*

Do-it-Yourself (DIY) biology's research communities emerge outside, or 'extra to', institutional laboratories, which is why I refer to this type of movement as 'extra-institutional science'. The movement is internet-native, but the evolution of communities is highly country-specific. In Canada, DIY biology raises hopes of a biotech revolution. In Germany, it is associated with a dystopian future of damaging pathogens escaping from the laboratories. Great Britain's approach is rather tolerant, and the country has become the movement's European epicentre. Policymakers, DIY biologists and publics are tasked with negotiating a configuration that is mutually desirable in their specific sociocultural context. This project examines why the boundary-challenging activities of extra-institutional science are so differently perceived and acted-upon. To do so, this project investigates how three different nation states, and their respective DIY communities, imagine themselves through extra-institutional science in keeping with their political cultures, goals and traditions. To this end, I foreground the tension between a controversial, globally networked DIY science movement, and the unique national socio-cultural contexts of implementation. I

draw on related work within the field of STS and specifically expand upon Jasanoff's conceptual work on sociotechnical imaginaries. I further draw on Star & Griesemer (1989) to conceptualise local DIY biology community laboratories as boundary objects, enabling me to investigate how DIY laboratories cause collisions across different social worlds, mobilize actors with sometimes divergent visions, thereby providing grounds for negotiation, normalization or rejection.

The Dearth of "Disability" in Experts' Discussion of Human Genome Editing *Dorit Barlevy, Baylor College of Medicine; Haley Manley, Baylor College of Medicine; Christopher Thomas Scott, Baylor College of Medicine*

Recent interest in human applications of genome editing has exploded. It is hoped that research and development of these technologies will potentially prevent or treat disease and disability. We interviewed 30 experts from a variety of disciplines inquiring about their perspectives on the present status and plausible futures of human genome editing. This paper analyzes those experts' discourse with respect to the concepts of disease and disability. Examination will focus on frequency and connotations of terms such as "disease," "illness," "condition," and "disability," with discussion exploring the tangle of concepts of nature, normality, and identity that easily blur distinctions between disease and disability. We propose using both social and biomedical models of disease and disability to gain a more comprehensive understanding of disease, disability, and the aims of medicine.

Session Organizers:

Dan Santos, Monash University (Australia)

Santiago J Molina, University of California Berkeley

Chair:

Dan Santos, Monash University (Australia)

385. "Throw Up for Good": Re-Materializing the Failures of Technocapitalism

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Silicon Valley's mantra of "Fail Better," a meme cut from a Samuel Beckett novella and pasted in many a coder's cubicle, still fuels the imaginations of young (mostly white and male) entrepreneurs. But the original passage is less about iterating toward start-up stardom than it is about absurd and abject physicality: "Fail again. Better again. Or better worse. Fail worse again. Still worse again. Till sick for good. Throw up for good." The novella's title, *Worstword Ho!*, aptly contextualizes the failures of technocapitalism, whose blind optimism and careless expansionism reveals some of the worst traits of a culture driven forward by colonial instincts. The discussants in this roundtable engage the burgeoning field of "failure studies" to offer alternative narratives for technocapitalism, focusing on topics of care and repair, including: 1) Techno-failure, from buffering time to planned obsolescence, as an economic principle; 2) Technofailures, misfits who can or will not adapt to the constant flow of new tech innovations; 3) Personal failure as a motivating factor in renegotiating the gendered politics of tech innovation. Informed by queer theory, new materialism, feminism, infrastructure studies, and decoloniality, these foci resist the myth of technological dematerialization while embracing the messiness of bodies, the vulnerability of minds, and the earthbound quality of all things technological. Discussants will present individual failure narratives, identify points of intersection, and ultimately recommend modes of resistance to technocapital toxicity, including research-creation interventions, critical pedagogies, and strategies for upsetting the epistemic asymmetries inherent in STEM-dominant cultural systems.

Presenters:

Neta Alexander, Colgate University

Daniela Rosner, University of Washington

Session Organizer:

Marcel O'Gorman, University of Waterloo, Canada

386. (Dis)Trust in Public Sector Data Infrastructures - II: Forensics and Fevers, Testing and Trust

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

STS scholarship on technopolitics typically examines the role that governments and state organizations play in producing, enabling, and leveraging data, technology, and science. Technocratic projects like conducting censuses, modeling weather, producing medicines, constructing computers or developing weapons serve both state and scientific masters. While the legitimacy of these investments are often intertwined with the legitimacy of state power, such power and legitimacy also relies upon scientific development and the sustained production of technoscientific imaginaries. Yet recent years have witnessed a range of governmental actions around the world designed to purposefully delegitimize states' technoscientific investments. Politicians work to dismantle state-funded scientific efforts, often under the guise of free-market commitments and austerity principles. The Covid-19 pandemic has revealed the global cost of distrust in public-sector science, technology, and data. Even as scientists produced a vaccine with unprecedented speed, governments around the world failed to track the spread of the virus, let alone provide data to enable decision-making. In some countries, political leaders are propagated conspiracies and "fake science", undermining public health and scientific development. Just as governments can help advance science, technology, and data, they may also choose to strategically curb such pursuits or actively undermine their legitimacy. This panel examines how public-sector technoscientific efforts are made legitimate, and how that legitimacy is strategically undermined. We ask, how are state-sponsored science and technology projects legitimated? How can this legitimacy come undone? How can trust in public-sector technoscience be repaired? This second session of 3 focuses on case studies related to forensics, medicine, and trust.

Participants:

Data Governance and the Temporal Construction of Forensic Evidence: The Making of the First Statewide Rape Kit Tracking Platform *Renee Shelby, Northwestern University*
Police management of sexual assault kits (SAKs) has led to systemic disorganization resulting in lost, forgotten, and abandoned forensic evidence. In response, advocates champion "sexual assault kit tracking platforms" as a pillar of rape kit reform. In 2017, Idaho became the first state to fully implement a statewide platform, the Idaho Sexual Assault Kit Tracking System (IKTS). While a step in confronting the systemic disorganization of evidence, SAK tracking platforms raise urgent questions about what governance paradigms, data relations, and discourses these systems enable. This paper asks: (1) How are discourses of "evidence" constructed in the legislative debate about IKTS? (2) What data relationships and governance paradigms do evidentiary discourses in IKTS enable? (3) How do evidentiary discourses draw on race, gender, and sexuality systems for meaning in IKTS? Using insights from critical race theory and STS, I answer these questions through a discursive analysis of state laws governing IKTS and SAK evidence, legislative committee hearings, annual reports to the legislature, IKTS protocols, and media coverage of Idaho's backlog between 2010 and 2020. I find concerns about "timeliness" and the temporal life of forensic evidence structured the creation and maintenance of IKTS. I argue timeliness is a data governance paradigm with multiple and shifting meanings of temporality that comprise various legal, social, and data relationships. The discourse of tardy, slow, and untimely forensic evidence is used to codify transparency and centralize legal decision making. By eliminating police discretion, IKTS protocols intervene into longstanding sexist and racist evidence testing decision-making. However, this intervention should not be read as a racial justice technofix.

Registers of Harm in the Sex Offender Registry *Jenny Brian, Arizona State University*

US sex offender laws are intended to prevent sexual violence,

identify potential perpetrators, and punish convicted perpetrators. The sex offender registry is deemed necessary as a means to empower communities because the data, the publicly available information, ostensibly allows families and individuals to protect themselves. The registry is widely accepted as a "legitimate" form of social control because the distribution of that information is accepted as a public good. This presentation poses a question: How does the sex offender registry create civil society? The registry reflects normative ideas about sexuality and health, seeks to produce responsible sexual citizens, and makes interventions into the notion of personhood itself — for victims and offenders. The sex offender registry is a public sector technology scripted with meanings of empowerment, but instead restricts freedom, disciplines bodies, and limits life chances. The registry, importantly, constructs criminality under the guise of safety and security. As a technology, the sex offender registry functions to amplify fear, obscure the real sources and sites of sexual violence, and displace attention (and resources) from real harms (Harkins 2020). Dismantling the ineffective registry and rejecting impositions of risk force us to ask painful questions about our desire to punish, surveil and banish, to attend to the actual realities of gendered and racialized sexual harm and the complex structural origins of sexual harm (Levine & Meiners 2020), to confront our fear of sexuality and notions of taboo and repression of benign variation (Hoppe 2014), and reckon with a deep and pervasive homophobia and transphobia.

Trivial Consent: Paradox and Production in Opposition to US Migrant DNA Testing *Elizabeth Dietz, Arizona State University*

A policy change went into effect in early 2020 requiring DNA collection from migrants entering the United States. Groups such as the ACLU released statements in opposition noting that DNA would be collected from migrants "without their consent." This critique appears to accurately reflect Department of Homeland Security procedures in place. However, it imagines a world in which such consent would transform relations of power between a migrant and the US government such that their expression of will could and would be respected; in other words, a world in which their consent would matter. In this talk, I argue that the kind of consent whose absence is used as opposition to the extractive, criminalizing harms of forced DNA collection would be, in practice, trivial. But its trivialness is significant: we ought to take seriously how consent is invoked as a key solution to problems of injustice. We must grapple with consent's constitutional importance, and how it can be deployed to shift liability away from the powerful, gesturing to a liberal valuation of individual autonomy while failing to acknowledge structural conditions that constrain it. The ACLU's argument about consent offers a window into the world that makes their position a reasonable and widely held one. Their civil rights and individual liberties advocacy draw upon broadly held and fundamental ethical tenets, but risk reproducing their limitations. This advocacy moment offers a window into how opposition, even in the spirit of justice, can uphold logics that underpin the practices we seek to dismantle.

Covid-19, Dengue Fever and Trust in Science: Findings from an Interview Study in Mexico *April Hovav, University of California at San Diego*

Trust in science is a topic of significant interest in the midst of the COVID-19 pandemic. Much of the existing literature seeks to identify individual-level characteristics, such as education level or political affiliation, that are correlated with higher or lower levels of trust in scientific expertise. Others take a historical approach, looking at the impact of macro-level societal changes on levels of trust in science within society. As STS scholars have argued, trust in science is complex and depends on the specific scientific endeavor in question. This study uses a novel approach to investigate the mechanisms through which a specific scientific endeavor is perceived as trustworthy or not by comparing the

same participant's reaction to three different public health measures: 1) existing measures for the prevention of Dengue fever, 2) the use of genetically modified mosquitoes for Dengue prevention, and 3) COVID-19 prevention measures. Drawing on 40 in-depth, semi-structured interviews with residents of Dengue endemic regions of Mexico, I argue that the following three factors impacted participants' level of trust: 1) personal experience with the disease, 2) perceived level of government involvement in the scientific process, and 3) the consistency of the available information. Furthermore, I found that one's trust in scientists' ability to produce safe and effective genetically modified mosquitoes to reduce incidences of Dengue did not predict one's trust in scientific information about COVID-19. This research contributes to our understanding of trust in science and the spread of health (mis)information.

Pushing the envelope: The development of a new testing technology in a Taiwan's lab during COVID-19 pandemic
YiXiang Shawn Sun, dept. of Geography, National Taiwan University

In 2020, the world was enveloped in the pandemonium COVID-19 has caused, with lockdown policies implemented in many countries. However, Taiwan, along with other few countries, remains almost virus-free. Unlike their counterparts that are heavily impacted by the pandemic, scientific labs in Taiwan are able to carry out research on testing technologies and vaccines at full tilt. Existing literature has predominately tried to shed light on the prevention measures that Taiwan's government adopted and its rapid response to crisis. This paper, conversely, seeks to advance our understanding of how to carry out scientific research in turmoil and in a non-Western context through the lens of a year-long ethnography from a mass spectrometry (MS) laboratory in Taiwan. Since MS is not primarily used for identifying virus, extra work is needed for the scientists to push the envelope. Inspired by Pickering (1995)'s concept of "dance of agency", this paper scrutinizes the development of such testing platform, capturing the back-and-forth interaction between the scientists and the instrument to see how it is made able to identify virus and therefore stabilize. The role the government plays during the development is also examined. Discussion is also on the social context in which such a dance is set, detailing how the scientists managed to secure research funding from the government, and mobilized research infrastructure and network. Based on the fieldwork, I argue that when examining how such dance of agency works or fail to work, temporal-spatial, material, and even bureaucratic circumstances are of great importance.

The Construction of the Mills-Reincke Phenomenon
Roan Parrish, Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University

How did early twentieth-century scientists create a public health phenomenon, only for it to be effectively abandoned a decade later until it resurfaced in the twenty-first century? In this paper, I look at the Mills-Reincke Phenomenon and the ways in which it was constructed from and contested with mortality statistics. Using Massachusetts Board of Health publications and journal articles from the 1870s to 1920s, I begin an investigation into how the collection of mortality statistics and the implementation of intermittent water filtration became woven together into a narrative about typhoid fever and deaths by other causes. The Mills-Reincke Phenomenon, first published in 1910, was both widely quoted and yet quickly contested by other sets of mortality statistics and case studies of introducing and removing water filtration systems. I approach this disagreement using STS literature on scientific controversy and production of knowledge through (limited means of) quantification; in particular, I emphasize how the same numbers can gain different meanings from the arguments in which they are used. I end my discussion by pointing to recent articles that have used this phenomenon as a rhetorical artifact outside of its original context. How does a concept built from attempting to utilize very specific statistics in ways which were under dispute even in its time leave this

nanced, complicated system to become a moral call to action in twenty-first century editorials?

Session Organizers:

Janet Vertesi, Princeton University
danah boyd, Microsoft Research / Data & Society
Alondra Nelson, Institute for Advanced Study, Princeton

387. Sense ecologies: new technologies and strategies of environmental surveillance - I

1:20 to 2:50 pm
4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Drones and mounted cameras monitoring wildfire ignitions. Satellites detecting areas of deforestation and reforestation or the transport of agents through ocean currents. Weather stations tracking humidity and rainfall surrounding monocrops. Video cameras poised to capture evidence of rare or threatened species, while bodies and wearable medical devices register the presence and passage of industrial pollutants. Sensors and modes of sensing are part of infrastructures that monitor and mobilize environments, constituting atmospheres of data, knowledge production, and world-making (Gabrys 2019). These 'sense ecologies' are differentially charged with promise when imagined and enacted (Spackman and Burlingame 2018), sometimes with expectations that they might deliver a world without surprises (Masco 2014). In practice, the promise of recent and new environmental sensing technologies are highly ambivalent. Their proliferation has been crucial to projects that hold powerful state and non-state actors to account, while (often concurrently) being enlisted as vectors for state securitization, targeted discrimination, corporatization and neoliberal intrusion (Mansfield 2008). Whatever their use, new sensing technologies are powerful, often compromised (Liboiron 2017), and are increasingly widespread means for imagining, constituting and intervening in environments. This open panel seeks contributions that examine new techno-imaginaries of environmental surveillance, including (but not limited to) analyses of sense ecologies and their 'good' or 'bad' relations, sites and practices of sensing, the promises of sensing technologies, ecologies of attuned sensing, distributed sensing networks, and the privatisation of sense ecologies. References: Gabrys, Jennifer. 2019. Sensors and Sensing Practices: Reworking Experience across Entities, Environments, and Technologies. *Science, Technology & Human Values* 44 (5):723-736. Liboiron, Max. 2017. Compromised agency: The case of BabyLegs. *Engaging Science, Technology, and Society*, 3, 499-527. Mansfield, Becky, ed. 2008. Privatization: property and the remaking of nature-society relations. Oxford: Blackwell. Masco, Joseph. 2014. The theater of operations: National security affect from the Cold War to the War on Terror. Durham, NC: Duke University Press. Spackman, Christy, and Burlingame, Gary. A. 2018. Sensory politics: the tug-of-war between potability and palatability in municipal water production. *Social Studies of Science*, 48(3): 350-371.

Participants:

Indian Ocean Colors *Vivian Y Choi, St. Olaf College*

Inspired by ethnographic accounts of disasters recounting the colors of the Indian Ocean shorelines in the Eastern Sri Lanka, this paper explores the hues of the Indian Ocean, as "good to think with and to live with" (Helmreich 2011). While oceans are almost always described and associated with the color blue, these descriptions of past disasters — the black sludgy waters of the tsunami and the red, blood-tinged sea from civil war-related violence — harken to the ocean as both symbolic and material. I consider these oceanic reflections alongside ocean color science, which, through remote sensing, charts the declining of phytoplankton in the rapidly warming Indian Ocean basin, changing its hues to a deeper green and, highlighting troubling ecological concerns for planetary life. Examining ocean colors in their multiple forms of collective memory and models for planetary destruction, for example, I denaturalize the ocean as inherently "blue," thus moving away from other naturalized assumptions of the ocean as conduits for capitalism and spaces of productivity as proposed in narratives of "blue economies" (see Schrader 2012). That is, I ask, what might a broader spectrum of ocean hues offer in contrast to dominant economic and security

narratives of bluing?

Sensing weather: anticipatory ecologies of meteorology, experiential forecasting, and small-scale farming in Western Kenya *Julian Rochlitz, University of Bonn*

Anticipatory knowledge about the weather is a vital element in livelihood activities that form material relations with the atmosphere. A prime example is agriculture, which is implicated in relations with rainwater, energy from the sun, and other atmospheric elements to grow plants. Based on an ethnographic case study of weather forecasting for and among smallholder farmers in Western Kenya, in this paper I am attending to the different ways in which the weather is sensed and registered as basis of knowing what atmospheric conditions to expect. While expert forecasts that draw on meteorological sensing technologies are promoted as a solution to dealing with emerging ecological change, I show how relating to the weather is an entangled affair in a sensory assemblage that simultaneously draws on scientific instruments and on more embodied sensoria that are associated with experiential knowledge. Building on concepts of mediation and thinking of the ecological in relational terms, I suggest the notion of epistemic proxies to treat the mediation of weather through scientific and experiential devices symmetrically. In practice, then, knowing the weather is ecological not only as a way of dealing with the material environment but also by building relations between different sensory devices and practices of interpretation. These include technological instruments, animals, clouds, dew, and other entities, which in everyday agricultural practice are mobilized together. It is therefore this combination of sensoria that mediates the weather as something to be known and acted upon.

Integrating Local Prevention Knowledge with (and about) Surveillance Technologies to Increase Resilience against Forest Fires in Spain. *elvira santiago, A Coruña University; Vincenzo Pavone, Consejo Superior Investigaciones Cientificas (CSIC)*

Forest fires constitute one of the main environmental threats in southern European countries. During 2019, in Spain only, there were a total of 10883 forest fires that burned 83963 hectares of land, which make Spain the country most affected in Europe, both in number of fires and in burned area. Given the severity of the socio-economic, political and ecological damage that natural disasters like forest fires cause each year, the international community designed action programs for disaster risk reduction (DRR). The current Sendai Framework (2015-2030) recognizes the need of coordinated action between local, national and international actors to strengthen risk governance, to invest in disaster risk, and to enhance disaster preparedness. With the view of improving resilience to natural hazards and achieve a full engagement of public and private actors into bottom-up initiatives oriented the mitigation of forest fires, the main objective of our nationally funded project, MitigACT (PID2019-1074443RA-I00), is to incorporate experiences and practices of different lay publics into DRR plans. Adopting an ANT perspective, our aim is further improve the current understanding of the concept of resilience by engaging different public and private actors in Canarias and Galicia (including farmers, firefighters, technology developers, decision makers, public authorities, CSOs) to a) study how they assess new surveillance technologies such as drones and location-based applications currently implemented to improve the mitigation of forest fires and b) to facilitate the co-design of alternative prevention strategies based on the regional cultural heritage and their local knowledge.

Virtual Olfaction: Reimagining Sensory Ecologies *Christy Spackman, SFIS - Arizona State University*

Over the past few decades, citizen science efforts have set in place the opportunity to shift whose forms of sensing and interacting with the environment matters. As many scholars note,

that promise often flounders in the face of institutional politics and knowledge infrastructures that dictate the circulation and validation of sensing technologies. This is especially true when environmental sensing—attunement to smells, tastes, or even affect (e.g. Calvillo 2018; Hoover 2017; Tironi 2018)—pits everyday and expert perceptual abilities. Bodies and their sensory capacities contribute to, or undo, contemporary ecologies of sensing. Recent enthusiasm for virtual reality as a space for experiential education or exploration, however, opens up the possibility for actively designing novel sensory ecologies. Such environments promise new distributed modes and networks of sensing. At the same time, virtual environments risk reifying what, exactly, is an environment. This paper examines an in-progress effort to apply Virtual Olfaction (VO; the delivery of dynamic olfactory cues into a virtual space) to the expert and everyday sensory labor (Spackman & Lahne 2019) of monitoring water quality. Even as VO offers new possibilities for democratizing and shifting the sensory politics associated with monitoring water quality, it brings forward new challenges: olfactants themselves can be toxic. As such, creating ecologies of attuned sensing within a VO interface necessarily activates additional levels of surveillance and substitution.

Session Organizers:

Timothy Neale, Deakin University

Will Smith, Deakin University

Chair:

Alex Zahara, Department of Geography, Memorial University

388. Altered States: Medicine, Madness, and Mysticism

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

As suggested by many public commentators, we are in the midst of a “psychedelic renaissance.” As regulations on both research and consumption begin to relax, substances such as LSD, MDMA, and psilocybin have re-emerged as both therapeutic panacea and fixtures on the cultural landscape. This panel makes sense of this contemporary moment by turning to the longer history of encounter between the sciences of the mind and “altered states of consciousness.” Indeed, techniques for altering perception have long been interwoven with the human sciences— from philosopher William James’ self-experimentation with nitrous oxide to psychiatrist Humphrey Osmond’s work with mescaline as a “model psychosis” (Dyck 2008). These techniques, chemical and otherwise, have been situated uneasily between discourses of modernity and tradition, science and religion, rationality and madness: the means through which the subject themselves might be, at once, transcended and rendered a proper object of scientific study. Accordingly, this panel refuses easy distinctions between medicine, religion and politics. While LSD and adjacent substances have been the subject of recent studies within both the history of science and science and technology studies (Langlitz 2012)(Breen 2019)(Hartogsohn 2020)(Jay 2019), this panel takes a wider scope: a consideration of “altered states” more broadly. In expanding the category of the psychedelic beyond the neuropharmacological, we bring in related phenomena, nitrous oxide and sensory deprivation, using this expanded frame to collectively historicize the mind as a scientific object through it’s perceived other: altered states.

Participants:

Mysticism, Mind-altering Drugs and Psychology: 1870-1919

Jacob Green, University of California Los Angeles

Since the ban on scientific research on psychedelic drugs was lifted 15 years ago, researchers at universities including Johns Hopkins and NYU have been investigating the relationship between psychedelics and mystical experience. While many cite work in the 1960s as the origins of this research, it actually has a much longer history stretching back to William James’ discussion of nitrous oxide intoxication in *The Varieties of Religious Experience* at the beginning of the 20th century. In this paper, I treat James as the central node in an epistolary and literary network in which psychologists, philosophers and

religious leaders communicated about their drug experiences. I will discuss psychological studies of mysticism that compared mystical experience to drug intoxication in order to discredit the authority and veracity of the claims of religious mystics. I will also explore how some philosophers used the sense of union with the oneness of creation which can sometimes be attained through breathing subanesthetic doses of nitrous oxide to argue against Hegel and his Dialectic. Additionally, I will discuss how Christians conceptualized the illuminating aspects of nitrous oxide and mescaline intoxication using the bible, sometimes claiming that Christ tapped into his divinely-given powers through entering states of consciousness similar to those produced by drugs. Overall, I hope to elucidate the relationship between drugs, humans and the divine in American intellectual circles around the turn of the 20th century.

The Cruel Optimism of Political Work: Public Debate about LSD as a Function of Professional Norms *Alexis Turner, Harvard University*

With the Cold War raging, American doctors and scientists searched for ways to turn their skills towards combating totalitarianism. For more than a few, LSD seemed to offer what they sought. But whether that technopolitical promise was because the altered states of consciousness LSD produced would sharpen political judgment, foster creativity, produce psychologically well-adjusted normalcy, produce psychologically well-adjusted rebellion, drive enemies to madness, or do covert service as a truth serum in the world of realpolitik was hotly contested. Ultimately, all the proponents' varying hopes were dashed. LSD and other psychedelics were classified as Schedule I substances in 1970, barring them from all use whatsoever, including for research and medical purposes. While these debates are often flattened as part of the boundary work involved in reinstating psychedelics as medical tools, reconstructing past disagreements in their depth and specificity reveals interesting parallels between localized modes of professional knowledge production and political action. In particular, I argue that divergences on the national stage arose as a result of relying on professional practices and norms in choosing practical political tactics. Debates within shared knowledge-making communities, in contrast, diverged over politically and theoretically substantive points. The result was what Lauren Berlant has dubbed a "cruel optimism" on both sides: while those whose professional norms favored acting in concert were more successful than those whose norms favored individuality, they were unable to convince politicians of their executive capacity to protect against the dangers they claimed the latter posed. The end result was blanket prohibition.

"In a Dark Room with Eyes Shut": Sensory Deprivation, Observation, and the Cold War Sciences of Mind *Jeffrey Mathias, Cornell University*

In 1953, confined to a small chamber for four days under the watchful eyes of a team of McGill psychologists, an experimental subject slipped into "a dream while awake." Their eyes hidden behind opaque goggles, the subject nonetheless saw something that, stranger still, gazed back: "a pair of spectacles, which were then joined by a dozen more, without wearers, fixed intently on me." This subject was a participant in an experiment in "perceptual isolation," a project that recast solitary confinement as a problematic of perception and monotony. Unexpectedly, many isolated subjects experienced vivid hallucinations, described as akin to those produced via mescaline, leaving the team of psychologists puzzled. What, if anything, were these hallucinations scientific evidence of? How might these uncanny visions render the psyche, in some fashion, visible? Located, in part, within the influx of clandestine funding for the human sciences from intelligence agencies during the early Cold War, perceptual isolation or "sensory deprivation," as it came to be known, was a sensation, inspiring dozens of replications in laboratories across North America. For scientists,

sensory deprivation was a method lodged between the brain and the unconscious: at once, an unstructured situation rendering "primary processes" legible via projection, much like the Rorschach test, and a "model psychosis," temporarily reproducing the symptoms of psychopathology for laboratory study. In this paper, I trace the interpretation of these hallucinations—as dream, as symptom, as neurological index—and the circulation of practices and instruments of witnessing and testimonial.

The Rhetorical Paradoxes of Psychedelic Experience and Ethos in Conspiratorialist-Fascist Construction of Evidence *Amanda Rose Pratt*

In this paper, I bring science and technology studies scholarship on psychedelics (Stark and Campbell, Corbin, Stamm, Noorani, Langlitz) into conversation with rhetorical scholarship (Anders, Nicotra, Doyle, Ceraso) to argue that a paradoxical mode of constructing evidence emerges from psychedelic rhetoric that has increasingly high stakes in the age of QAnon shamans and neoliberal psychedelia. The rhetorical paradox of ineffability emerges because psychedelic experiences are often characterized by both ineffability and noetic qualities; resulting in an experience so profound that many feel compelled to attempt to communicate despite the experience transcending description. This leads to the second rhetorical paradox, of psychedelic ethos: credibility is inherently called into question both because of the altered state of consciousness induced by psychedelics and the mystical nature of revelatory insight. This paradox is compounded because on one hand, psychedelics are known to subvert the ego, but on the other hand, noetic experiences of "objective truths" can result in an inflated sense of ethos. As a result, genres of psychedelic discourse emerge from these paradoxes that are—to varying degrees, with varying relative levels of credibility, and incurring various degrees of impact and harm—inherently invested in the enterprise of rhetorical science and technology studies. Through a case study of psychedelic fascism, I illustrate how a commitment to the "panacea" narrative that psychedelics produce universally "good relations" ignores the significant role of psychedelic experience and ethos in the ever-growing world of "conspirituality"—an online movement driving the contemporary crisis around information literacy in New Age wellness discourse.

Session Organizer:

Jeffrey Mathias, Cornell University

Chair:

Erika Dyck, University of Saskatchewan

389. Plenary - Black Technoscience

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: Auditorium

Plenary - Black Technoscience

Participant:

Black Technoscience Beth Coleman, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

Black Technoscience

Session Organizer:

Beth Coleman, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Ruha Benjamin, Princeton University

390. Feminists of Color Science Studies – Building social infrastructure through a feminist BIPOC network

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

In this open panel we invite the participation of feminist BIPOC scholars to reflect on our varied entrée and engagement with science studies and to build a network to amplify and connect our work. In order to grapple with our core commitments, position ourselves in relation to STS, and recognize

scholarship to which we have applied indigenous, Black, women of color, post-/decolonial, transnational, dis/ability and queer/trans feminisms, we focus on building good relations and a feminist ethics of care through a network. In this space we seek to acknowledge and connect across differing points of entry into STS, which begin with sets of questions, concerns, practices, and solutions driven as much by critical political inquiry as feminist constructivist approaches within science and technology studies. Our work tends to amplify epistemic violence, intersectionality, and normative justice concerns. We are often interested in the ways that technology, science, and medicine have interacted with the bodies of BIPOC and projects that forward the radical liberation of BIPOC. We seek contributions and conversation from feminist BIPOC scholars about their entry into the field, including the arts, scholarship, or types of activism that inspired you to engage with STS; what you think distinguishes the work of feminists of color within STS; and how we bring the field forward by building a feminists of color sciences studies network for mutual support, ideas generation, and to connect to others whom we suspect do work that overlaps in this area but might not see themselves as engaging STS.

Participants:

Feminist STS at the End of the World *Cristina Visperas, University of Southern California*

We have more feminist theories and critical theories of race than ever, and yet I wonder how of much that has been deployed to radically transform the increasingly corporate university? Rather than answering this question, I want to revitalize its stakes through a discussion about the end of the world. An unprecedented emergency against which leading climate scientists unreservedly propound civilizational change (IPCC, 2018), the problems of global warming and mass extinction not only vex our scientific and humanistic tools for understanding them, but also weigh heavy on our public and personal feelings toward (the value of) human and nonhuman life. How does one stay present with an unthinkable future, whose scale of suffering is described as “incalculable” and “catastrophic” (Scientists’ Statement of Support for Non-Violent Direct Action Against Government Inaction Over the Climate & Ecological Emergency, 2019). Change at every level of society - change for which we have no precedent in human history - is what climate scientists and activists are calling for. But what does civilizational change look like in our academic practices? Rather than gesturing towards new theory, or towards more and more theory as the university demands, this paper argues for making do with the promises of our long-held intersectional feminist traditions. For us, civilizational change does not mean invention but remediation.

Girls, Gadgets and Gatekeepers: A Case Study for Envisioning Decolonial, Feminist Approaches To STS Projects *Isha Bhallamudi, University of California, Irvine*

As a female sociologist from the Global South, my entry point into STS was through my MA project, where I conducted an intersectional, feminist analysis of gendered and classed surveillance experienced by adolescents within the home, and the ways in which this shapes unequal access to digital technology. My paper was based on a mixed-methods study of 59 group interviews and 278 surveys conducted with 9th-grade adolescents in Mumbai, India. For this Open Panel, I wish to open up questions around feminist fieldwork, epistemic violence, ethics, privacy, confidentiality and North-South relations that emerged during this project. In the paper, I employ an autoethnographic approach to explore questions around IRB/Global North definitions of safety, privacy, confidentiality and informed consent, which don’t translate well in practice. For example, many of my research participants wanted credit for their responses, which was incompatible with the IRB requirement of anonymity. I also grappled with tensions over whether to use data that was technically collected with consent, but which felt like it was imparted as private confidential information imparted with trust. Class was a major factor, as lower-class adolescents were not groomed in the language of privacy and informed consent,

and did not edit responses accordingly. Imperatives of privacy, ethics and confidentiality therefore play out differently for different vulnerable groups, complicating what the IRB considers ethical fieldwork. What might a caring, decolonial, feminist, approach to STS research and network-building look like in this context? Using my experience as a case study, I offer some ideas and starting points.

We are Both the Settlers and the Colonised: The Messiness of Solidarity and Separation in Technoscientific Fieldwork *Kirsty Anantharajah; Jenna Harb, Australian National University*

In response to Navarro, Williams, and Ahmad’s (2013) call to ‘sit at the Kitchen Table’—highlighting the transformative potentialities of curating spaces where WOC can safely share and reflect on their experiences in the academy—we, two junior feminist BIPOC scholars, engage in a conversation of situation (Haraway 1988). What do the locations of our identities as Palestinian-Canadian and Tamil-Australian feminist researchers imply for the entwinement of power and knowledge in our respective research exploring digitised welfare in Lebanon, and the challenges of climate finance in Fiji? Drawing on an ethnography of our education and fieldwork experiences, this presentation seeks to foster discussion on the inherently complex, messy, and shifting nature of our identities and positionalities as feminist BIPOC researchers. We apply Chela Sandoval’s (1984) ‘oppositional consciousness’ to our daily spaces and relations in STS, posing questions on navigating race in schoolwork and in the field, default settings and selective (in)visibilities in academic training, and enduring binaries in foundational modes of thought—all of which, we argue, bear disproportionate burdens to feminist BIPOC scholars by sustaining logics of White Supremacy that interleave to render us both oppressed and complicit in oppression, to form our identities as both the colonised and the settler (Villenas 1996). Our presentation thus contributes to existing critical feminist STS literature on the dilemmas of researcher relationships, reflexivity, and privilege. In the spirit of the Kitchen Table, we hope that sharing our experiences may contribute to vital dialogue between feminist BIPOC scholars in support of ‘good relations’.

Navigating the White academy: How women of colour exist, resist and persist in educational institutions *Nadia Qureshi, OISE, University of Toronto*

In this paper I examine experiences navigating academic institutions as the site of my doctoral studies, that continue to perpetuate harms and inequities upon women of colour conducting research on race and STEM. Using Critical Race Theory (Ladson-Billings & Tate, 2006; Solórzano et al., 2000) as a theoretical framework, this paper seeks to illuminate how women of colour exist, resist and persist in educational institutions that continue to uphold structures of White patriarchal supremacy. Educational institutions in Canada are a relic of our colonial history, continually perpetuating systemic oppressions in society (Knight, 2019). In the field of STEM, inequities are exacerbated for Black and Brown bodies, where historical legacies of racism are not challenged (McGee, 2021). As a settler on this land, a woman of colour, and a science teacher – I entered doctoral studies to examine inequities in accessing STEM for people of colour. Throughout this journey, I have been unable to reconcile being a part of the hegemonic, colonial, academic institution and scholarship in the area of racial justice. In this autoethnographic study, I examine my own journals and experiences in my doctoral studies. I use inductive coding to establish themes on the barriers women of colour face in the academy researching race and STEM. Preliminary results pose that maintaining mental health, solidarity with other women of colour and oppressed people and mentorship are central components of navigating the White academy.

Session Organizers:

Rajani Bhatia, University at Albany, SUNY
Gwen D'Arcangelis, Skidmore College

391. Digital (Un)wellness: Power, Health, and Screen Time - III

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Participants:

Addictive or Curative? Video Games that Resist Hegemonic Mental Health Knowledge Toward Reimagining Crip Technoscience Futures *Jeff Nicklas, University of California, San Francisco*

The World Health Organization recently defined gaming disorder as a mental illness (WHO 2018). At the same time, companies and labs are designing video games and receiving FDA approval for games as prescription medicine. This paper applies Crip Technoscience (Hamraie and Fritsch 2019) to a close reading of the video game *Celeste*, where players step into the shoes of the game's protagonist, Madeline, as they are tasked with the seemingly impossible challenge of climbing the formidable Celeste Mountain while simultaneously grappling with Madeline's own struggles with anxiety and depression. *Celeste* engenders the core commitments of Crip Technoscience through the ways that Madeline must work to (re)make the world around her and how the game, as a technological artifact, helps build collectivities of new imaginaries around mental health. Rather than viewing games as being addictive or as providing a technological fix for mental health, *Celeste* shows that mental illness does not always need a cure and that mental health is core to the self. In these ways, *Celeste* imagines new ways to be and make access in our world. This paper adds to ongoing studies in critical game studies and emerging critical lenses within STS like Crip Technoscience by showing how games can simultaneously bring to light hegemonic discourse around mental health and disability while (re)imagining new worlds that shake and disrupt these discourses to their core.

Constructing Technology Uses Good for the Well-being of Visually Impaired Children *Emeline Brule*

Disabled children occupy a paradoxical position in public and professional discourses about childhood and technologies. Being disabled, using technologies is framed as necessary to their independence, education and future career, or in other words necessary to their future well-being as defined by their ability to fit in; Being children, using technologies is always potentially a threat to their education and socialisation; Being disabled children, using technologies put them at heightened risks of online abuse. How then do children and educators negotiate adequate uses of technologies and technologies to use? And what can we learn from this case of heightened surveillance, and increased concerns about children's vulnerability and development, about the interplay between expert discourses and situated decisions about technology uses? To explore these questions, we build on a two-years ethnographic study in a French organisation providing support services to visually impaired children, complemented with interviews and media coverage of disabled children and use of technologies. First, this case study challenges how we think about screens, to encompass tactile and audio interfaces. Visual interfaces are particularly tightly controlled due to their range of potential uses. Limiting functionality is a main way professionals and parents enforce a clear demarcation between good and bad technologies, although they often fail to notice the full range of (mis)uses. Second, it highlights the importance of temporal scales in current discourses and understandings of digital well-being. Finally, it demonstrates how children may advocate for their uses of technologies, drawing on these different discourses to make their case.

Deconstructing "digital wellbeing": Towards a critical conceptualization *Mora Matassi*

Digital wellbeing, broadly understood as reaching an "optimal"

balance with mobile technologies, represents a key site of moral and ethical conflicts regarding connected lives. In order to contribute to recent theoretical discussions on its conceptualization, this paper proceeds with a two-step strategy. First, it reviews three key theoretical roots to digital wellbeing—technologies of the self and regimes of living, addiction rhetoric, and wellness. Second, through discourse analysis, it identifies four main discursive communities where the term has circulated in different ways and for diverse purposes—technology companies; the niche of NGOs that contests technology companies; academia in communication and media studies; and the computer-human interaction community. The paper finds that digital wellbeing generally emerges top-down. Specifically, from a rather paternalistic perspective, the identified communities activate narratives aimed at either warning, nudging, helping, advising, modeling, or building for users. Two paradoxes are thus produced. First, digital wellbeing constructs a subject-as-user who can both fall into the traps of digital connectivity while being able to optimize her behavior. Second, it reinforces a paradoxical notion of the collective, whereby mediated sociality should be ultimately managed at the individual level. Finally, I argue that studies around digital wellbeing have primarily focused on the Global North, without considering how moral and ethical aspirations to a "good" life with technology might be shaped by precarious conditions of existence cutting across online and offline worlds. The paper aims to contribute to discussions in science and technology studies by examining the politics of knowledge constructed around lives lived digitally.

Seeking to de-script digital media for mental wellbeing:

Experiences of people with eating disorders *Paula Saukko, Loughborough University; Helen Malson, University of West of England*

Research on digital media and eating disorders (EDs) frequently focuses on detrimental effects of social media on body image. Our presentation moves beyond influence of images. Drawing on Madeleine Akrich's work we analyse how digital media inscribe relations between people, users and creators and institutions of mental health care and how users with EDs seek to de-script those relations to enhance mental wellbeing. Interviews with people with EDs (n=31) conducted in 2020 featured three themes. First, digital media enabled participants to connect with friends and family for companionship, but the media push toward broad and constant connectivity fuelled social comparisons and overwhelming interaction. Second, participants followed mainstream, recovery and body positive content creators and some created content themselves trying to curate a feed that would help them to accept themselves amidst commercially informed conventions flaunting competitive success. Third, the digital media offer of mental health support groups, apps, broadcasts and official and informal or gig telecare provided participants a variety of support but also led to paywalls, contradictory or dangerous experiences and stratified care. We conclude that digital media's potential to create interpersonal, peer and care relations based on companionship, sharing support and generosity is undercut by their economic impetus to maximise connectivity, commercialism, competition and efficiency. Akrich's focus on relations facilitated by technologies helps to move beyond media influence toward analysing digital media's role in broader interpersonal, mental health care and media-economic networks.

The construction of digital wellbeing during the COVID-19 pandemic *Artur de Matos Alves, Tele-Universite du Quebec; Ana Jorge, Lusófona University, Lisbon, Portugal; Inês Amaral, Coimbra University, Coimbra, Portugal*

This paper examines the discursive construction of "digital wellbeing" by examining the initiatives undertaken by mobile media platforms (such as Facebook, Apple and Google services) promoting screen time management and life-work balance during

the COVID-19 pandemic. In order to address the co-construction of digital platforms and public discourse on “wellbeing”, we employ multimodal critical discourse analysis (MCDA) methods (Machin and Mayr 2012, Fairclough 2012; Van Dijk 2005). We analyse the discursive and rhetorical framing of wellbeing and “time well spent” in verbal and non-verbal communications in the companies’ public relations and interface design. We argue that these companies have modulated their “digital wellbeing” discourse and practices by introducing features or services in response to the sanitary crisis and the impacts of confinements and remote work. Initiatives include the partnership between Google and Apple for the creation of a COVID-19 contact tracing framework, or “COVID-19 digital wellbeing toolkits” by Google and Facebook. Such actions extend the response to the “techlash” of 2017-2018, tackling the issues of ‘information overload’ (Levitin, 2014), ‘digital overconsumption’ (Gui, Fasoli, & Carradore, 2017), ‘social media fatigue’ (Bright, Kleiser, & Grau, 2015) and ‘technostress’ (Lee, Lee, & Suh, 2016) as part of “digital health”. The paper highlights the centering of a personal responsibility ethos in wellbeing discourse, while also discussing the reinforcement of chronological inequalities (Sharma 2017) and structural differences in screen time management and availability of leisure. This study contributes to debates on “wellbeing” and “productive time” constructed in discourse and enacted or codified in digital media platforms.

Session Organizers:

Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley

Alex Beattie, Victoria University Wellington

Laura Calloway, Indiana University

Chad Valasek, University of California at San Diego

392. Good Governance, Good Relations and (Nuclear) Waste Management II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Too often technical experts and government officials have seen the management and disposition of (nuclear) waste as a problem to be solved by experts, with the solution then “sold” to the broader public through techniques of public relations that are often so transparently manipulative as to be self-undermining. Instead of seeing waste management and disposition as narrowly technical problems to be resolved through techniques of quantitative risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis, they should be reframed as “wicked problems” (Churchman 1967, Rittel and Webber 1973) with the potential to disrupt good relations across a number of sociotechnical planes: between neighbors; between indigenous and settler populations; between corporations and local communities; between scientists and the public; and between state and society. Is it possible to solve these problems without toxic social consequences? We call on colleagues to draw on STS and the knowledge of its multiple ancillary disciplines to imagine sociotechnical processes that could build good social, political, and environmental relations. This might involve critique of existing processes, reportage of innovative improvements, or advocacy of novel processes. It will surely involve multi-perspectival visioning. Our primary interest is in nuclear waste, but we will entertain proposed papers on other waste forms as well.

Participants:

Building consensus in Italy: The national nuclear repository and the crisis of democracy *Davide Orsini, Rachel Carson Center, LMU Munich*

On January 5, 2021 SOGIN, the public company in charge of nuclear plant decommissioning and waste disposal in Italy, released the map of suitable sites for the emplacement a national repository. The document that a committee of experts redacted in 2014 on the basis of “objective criteria,” remained secret until 2020. The publication of CNAPI (National Map of Potentially Idoneus Sites) is the first step toward the implementation of a roadmap that has a twofold objective: promoting consultation with local communities and removing the (perceived)

arbitrariness of site selection. The first reactions are not promising: many municipalities from potentially idoneus areas—as indicated in the map—have already expressed their refusal to host the national repository and the association of Italian comuni asked the government to extend the period of time at their disposal for the elaboration of written objections and observations. Municipalities that already host decommissioned nuclear power plants (NPP) and facilities instead resist the implementation of the plan because they fear that with the construction of a national repository, they will lose the generous indemnities received over the past thirty years. This paper examines the roadmap established by SOGIN and the first reactions of local communities to its implementation to gain insights into the sociotechnical conflicts that surround the Italian repository project.

Deep Time Reckoning: Epistemic Excess & Infiniton Among Finland’s Nuclear Waste Experts *Vincent Ialenti, University of British Columbia*

Finland’s nuclear waste repository “safety case” experts have developed several portfolios of technical evidence to persuade the country’s nuclear regulatory authority, STUK, to certify the construction and operation of what will likely become the world’s first spent nuclear fuel repository. To do so, they combined techniques of analogical reasoning, quantitative modeling, qualitative scenario-making, mechanical stress testing, and geological fieldwork to make tentative projections about distant future geophysical, hydrological, and ecological happenings. Drawing on 32 months of fieldwork, this talk approaches the safety case’s epistemic excesses - its hyperconstructions of far future glaciations, climate changes, earthquakes, and human-animal interactions - not solely as fantasy documents devised to manipulate gullible stakeholders into consent. While the safety case was, indeed, made to persuade, its authors saw their radically farsighted inquires as flawed-but-pragmatic projections borne out of reflexive self-critique, multi-perspectival visioning, and iterative revision cycles. By adopting an outlook of infiniton - in which radical complexity was allowed to overflow the thoughts that thought it (Levinas 1969) - they distilled fragmentary sequences of hopes, calculations, fears, datasets, dreams, models, and anxieties about Finland’s socio-ecological futures into mundane artifacts of technocratic paperwork. With these creative labors in view, this talk asks whether the safety case can be recast as a generative starting point for envisioning more just socio-ecological relations with future human and non-human communities in Northern Europe and beyond.

National Specificities in “Safetization”: Decision-Making on Nuclear Waste Management in Finland and France *Markku Lehtonen, Universitat Pompeu Fabra; Matti Kojo, University of Tampere; Mika Kari, Tampere University; Tapio Armas Litmanen, University of Jyväskylä*

While both are seen as forerunners in final disposal of nuclear waste, Finland and France display striking differences in terms of the ways in which safety of the repository projects is discussed in public and policy. By analysing selected key parliamentary debates on the final disposal of nuclear waste, this paper examines how Finnish and French parliamentarians frame, politicize and depoliticize safety. The paper adopts as the central concept “safetization” in decision-making on nuclear waste management. Safetization refers here to a process whereby 1) images of risks and uncertainties are either created or explained away to give assurance of safety, and 2) current practices are normalized or various changes to current practices are demanded in order to ensure safety. Safetization can hence either support or challenge the prevailing views of safety, i.e., either reinforce trust and confidence, or open up the debate in order to generate more robust understandings on the issue. “Safetization” redistributes political power between key actor groups such as implementers,

regulators, and politicians. We illustrate how power is exercised via safetization and de-safetization in public and policy debate on nuclear waste, in ways similar to the politicization and de-politicization processes in energy policy more generally. Alongside topics such as energy security and climate change mitigation, safetization deserves a place on energy governance agenda. For STS, safetization provides a concept for analysing the subtle power play that conditions the “good relations” amongst societal groups seeking to get to grips with nuclear waste governance.

Visions of Nuclear Landscapes: Official Expertise and Common Sense in Planning for Marking Waste Repositories *Rosemary Joyce, University of California, Berkeley*

This paper builds on critical examination of the way that the US government developed proposals to mark nuclear waste repositories, currently the Waste Isolation Pilot Plant in New Mexico, as well as Yucca Mountain in Nevada, currently suspended but not definitively canceled. Examining recursive cycles of thinking by government-designated “experts”, some of which include projected imaginations of a non-expert public, a variety of imagined understandings of the places proposed for these projects emerges. These nuclear landscapes are uneasily balanced between a concept of a kind of terra nullius, a landscape emptied of human presence, and what others call a “national sacrifice zone”, a space seen as available to be used with regret, despite the presence of a small number of people. I argue that the experts project a kind of common sense about places they imagine as deserted, and assume would be shared by broader publics. The presentation juxtaposes this imagined vision of desert with two forms of alternative visions of these places, one drawn from indigenous activists mobilized to oppose these projects in Nevada, and one drawn from creative work by artists. In both cases, alternative forms of communication of the presence of nuclear waste and the potential dangers that buried wastes might entail position the broader population as potentially responsive to these sites in ways that contrast strikingly with the expert imagination of the Federal planners. The paper ends by considering how these contrasts might guide thinking about engagement in considering this “wicked problem” and its potential remediation.

Session Organizer:

Allison Macfarlane, George Washington University

Chair:

Allison Macfarlane, George Washington University

393. Knowing Platforms - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Participants:

A platform for academic integrity: power and the ethics of care in online proctoring *Martin Oliver, UCL Institute of Education; Jade Vu Henry, Goldsmiths, University of London*

This paper explores the ethico-political entanglements of platforms, discussing a case that focuses on students’ academic integrity, and reflecting on the conceptual and practical challenges of knowing platforms. From the starting point of once recorded incident – a young woman in tears, having failed an exam because an online proctoring platform classified her actions as cheating – we studied the ways in which an algorithm became entangled in and refracted (Christin, 2020), or perhaps defracted (Østerlund et al, 2020), through its relations with different people. These include the design of the proctoring platform, the alliances and oppositions that formed around it, and the different ways of knowing about students’ integrity that were drawn into competition as a consequence. Our analysis is structured using Tronto’s registers of care (1993), which allow us to follow the platform through its role in ‘EdTech’ power networks

(Williamson, 2019), into debates about institutional reputation, to contestation about its relationship to pedagogy, and back to the ways that students respond to its use. We use this analysis to show how power is enacted in who cares, what they care about, but also in the quality of caring relations. Drawing on Heidegger, we show how the quality of care advocated by the company that owns the platform created control and dependency. However, rather than simply rejecting or condemning the platform, we suggest new alliances and reconfigurations (Suchman, 2007) that could be constituted between students and the platform, revisiting historic ideas of academic integrity and honour codes.

Assembling solidarity Exploring tactics for opening the black box of delivery platforms in times of COVID19 in Colombia *Derly Sanchez, Derly Sánchez; Oscar Maldonado, Universidad del Rosario*

Digital platforms are opaque not only for researchers but also for workers and users. This paper discusses the methodological and analytical challenges of studying work conditions of digital delivery workers attached to the delivery platform Rappi in Bogotá (Colombia) in the times of COVID19 and the efforts of cooperation between a research team interested in analysing health and working conditions of delivery work and the Colombian movement of digital workers (MNRD, acronym in Spanish). Rappi is an ‘on-demand delivery startup’ active in Latin America. Just in Colombia, it has 1,500 direct employees and more than 25,000 associated delivery workers (Rappitenderos), many of them Venezuelan migrants. Since last year some of those ‘associates’ have been taking to the streets to protest against the precarious working conditions of the delivery work: such as long working hours, distances and fixed tariffs which have led to decreasing incomes, accounts’ suspensions as well as constant scrutiny from external (police) and internal security employees (Rappi brigadistas), safety problems plus the lack of basic social security. Drawing on Michele De Certeau’s concept of tactics (1984), we reflect on the encounters between researchers and workers to develop techniques and reflexive data practices to understand the platform control and operation strategies. The result of this interaction has been a methodological assemblage that gathers WhatsApp dialogues and observations, joining street demonstrations and helping the workers movement to build evidence by producing numbers about their work, the risk that they face and the value they create.

Knowing/Being Known by Platforms: From Authentic to Authenticated post-#GamerGate *Nelanthi Hewa; Christine H. Tran, University of Toronto*

While platforms may be hard to know, they are increasingly invested in knowing—and policing—users. From “verified accounts” to “two-factor authentication,” platform affordances have proffered metrics of “authenticity” as an antidote to the uncertainties of attention economies, which are ostensibly saturated by fake news, misinformation, and algorithmic radicalization (Haimson & Hoffman, 2016; Caplan, 2020). Yet the platformization of realness claims are often weaponized against the most marginalized, as evidenced by recent events like Pornhub’s demonetisation of unverified accounts. Early hashtag harassment events like #GamerGate foreshadowed the gendered consequences of digital realness regimes. In the ascent of “verified account” castes and other digital authenticators, the traditional “black box” conceptualization of platforms rings increasingly untrue. Rather, we argue, the algorithmic reality for marginalized users better resembles Wile E. Coyote’s painted tunnels on the side of mountains: vortexes of selective porosity that invite some roadrunners and flatten others. Through a Critical Discourse Analysis of #GamerGate coverage from 2014 and 2015, we attend to how ideologies of “realness” reproduce along gendered and racialized lines. Our paper builds on recent work on how the ideation of “realness” embeds forms of communicative and audience-managing labour among networked

creators (Abidin 2016; Banet-Weiser, 2012; Duffy, 2017). The ascent of “authentication-as-safety” is historicized within the hashtag harassment event “GamerGate,” our case study and pivotal moment in the platform veracity ecosystem when influencers and journalists were exhorted to authenticate their lives or lose their livelihoods. Everyone on the internet knows you’re a dog. Now what?

Knowing by Proxy: Search Engine Optimization on the Marketplace of Ideas *Chris Hesselbein, Cornell University STS; Malte Ziewitz, Cornell University*

Search engines like Google play a central role in answering a wide variety of questions. While their black-boxed methodology for ranking web pages has proven powerful for uncontested knowledge, problems arise in areas of in which the relevance and authoritativeness of information is unclear or contested. In the case of health-related queries, for example, medical information portals and pharmaceutical companies compete with providers of alternative medicine and anti-vaccination activists. In these situations, search engines struggle to algorithmically distinguish authoritative from less authoritative information—not least because search results are not only determined by the engine, but also by a shadow industry of search engine optimization (SEO) consultants, whose expertise is in making websites more visible in search results. In this paper, we present a qualitative study of how webmasters and SEO consultants in the field of healthcare navigate this confluence of commercial, informational, and political considerations. Focusing on the 2018 Medic Update – implemented by Google to promote websites based on their expertise, authoritativeness, and trustworthiness – we examine how webmasters and SEO consultants develop and operationalize knowledge of the search engine even in the absence of a clear set of criteria. Our study demonstrates that even though search platforms are ‘opaque’ and ‘inscrutable,’ they are neither unknowable nor impervious to outside influence. Understanding how social actors make information (in)visible in search results challenges the conventional ‘asocial’ narrative of how platforms operate, and sheds light on the practices (both human and algorithmic) that (de)stabilize the boundaries of knowledge on search platforms.

Session Organizer:

Moira Weigel, Northeastern University

394. Art, Science and Technology Studies - IV: Methods in Art and Science

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Chairs: Hanna Rose Shell

Participants:

Climate Science As Seen By Artists *Kris Decker, Zurich University of the Arts; Barbara Preisig, Zurich University of the Arts (ZHdK)*

Some while ago, science studies scholars could pride themselves of being unique in their attempts to observe climate scientists at work. Nowadays, it is not uncommon to meet an artist at the places where climatic changes are a matter of epistemic concern. Equipped with variegated interests, concepts, techniques, and sensibilities, artists are able to conduct fieldwork by other means and come up with materials that border on STS accounts (or keep these accounts aside). In our contribution, we will discuss a few exemplary projects from the arts and engage with their — oftentimes implicit — methodological peculiarities. How do artists put their perspectives on climate science into practice? What modes of observation and description might they add to the toolbox of science studies? And how could they make us think differently about scientific knowledge and about its problematization beyond the boundaries of professional communities?

Human Germline Gene Editing is Bioart: An open letter to Lulu

and Nana *Adam Zaretsky, NADLinc*

Transgenic Human Genetic Modification Babies can be designed along a wide variety of Aesthetic gene expression action plans. Considering the true range of germline expressionism possible in a collage of multiple genomic palettes, and considering the life span of GMO humans as time-based, new-media sculptures, we should critically question the use of health, enhancement, economic efficiency or even popular (domestic) culture to drive acceptable GMO baby design. Culture, health, enhancement, and profitability are neither simple concepts nor should they be our only deciding forces for future embodied design. What lies beyond public acceptance of the technology? Have Lulu and Nana's lives been offered up in order to ameliorate the leveling influences of public trends, medical bias and marketed anti-diversity?

Beer portraits: art-based research into digital assemblages in more-than-human worlds. *Tomi Slotte Dufva, Aalto-University, the school of Arts, Design and Architecture*

Digital: code, data, algorithms, machine learning is everywhere. However, whereas digital is ubiquitous, it is not always clear what is meant with the digital. Digital may be hard to grasp, and therefore (post)digital discussions may become fuzzy, one-sided, or abstract. Moreover, the comprehension of digital is unequal and depended for example on socio-economic statuses as well as location. In other words, digital takes place in different ways in different places and situations. We are entangled in the more-than-human worlds that include biological and technological, or more specific, computational assemblages. These entanglements are both mundane and uncanny, commonplace and novel at the same time. Moreover, the physical parts of such entanglements, hardware and networks, often consume generous amounts of energy and natural resources still remaining invisible. This research aims to portray the complex figurations of digital and material and think of the digital from a more-than-human position through art-based experiment. Inspired by Hayles's thoughts on bio- and cybersymbiosis along with feminist scholars like Myers and Basset, Kember & O'Riordan attempts to think paths out of the Anthropocene, this research works towards presenting alternative figurations on how to comprehend digital. Through art-based experiments with robots that draw based on fermentation data, the article aims to picture post-digital assemblages that contain both biological and technological actors. The research strives to provoke us to rethink the comprehension and readings of the post-digital assemblage and seek out new possibilities to do, make and think with the digital.

Stock Images of Artificial Intelligence: a quali-quantitative analysis *Alberto Romele, University of Tuebingen; Dario Rodighiero, Harvard University; Olivier Buisson, INA (Institut National de l'Audiovisuel); Claude Mussou, INA (Institut National de l'Audiovisuel); Marta Severo, University Paris Nanterre*

This presentation is not about the relationships between art, science, and technology, but about cultural productions that are considered neither artistic nor scientific. We refer to stock images, that is, pre-produced images made available for license by paying a fee to both the creators and stock agencies. In particular, we focus on stock images that represent Artificial Intelligence (AI). Our first hypothesis is that although usually disregarded by art and science, these images play a fundamental role in the constitution of the sociotechnical imaginaries about AI. Our second hypothesis is that not only these images might learn something from art and science, but also that art and science may benefit from their stereotyped way to represent reality. The presentation is developed in two stages. In the first stage, we propose a theoretical reflection on AI's representability. In the second stage, we propose a quali-quantitative analysis of 8,000 images resulting from the search “Artificial Intelligence” on Shutterstock, one of the major online

catalogs in the market of stock imagery. We resort to Snoop, an AI-based visual search engine developed by INA (the French National Audiovisual Institute) and Inria (the French National Institute for Research in Digital Science and Technology). Our presentation aims to contribute to STS by (1) further developing the existing debate on the sociotechnical imaginaries in innovation processes; (2) engaging in a critical discussion with the existing literature on representation in scientific and technical practices, and (3) proposing an original method to categorize and analyze images.

The art and science of chronobiology: A case study in triangulating a multidisciplinary ASTS project *Kristin Hussey, Medical Museion, University of Copenhagen; Louise Whiteley, CBMR and Medical Museion, University of Copenhagen; Isabella Martin, Independent artist*

There are various well-established paradigms for the encounter between art and science – from art as a tool for science communication, education, and the broadening of audiences, to science as a source of material and method for art. Both ‘directions’ have been criticized as instrumentalizing the other. A growing number of authors including Hannah Star Rogers, Megan Halpern, and Trevor Pinch have suggested that one way of deepening reciprocal engagement is the introduction of a third, STS perspective to this traditionally ‘two way’ encounter. In this paper, we present just such a triangulated, multidisciplinary project. Z-Time interrogates the methods and practices of circadian science at the Novo Nordisk Foundation Center for Basic Metabolic Research (CBMR), in embedded collaboration with university museum Medical Museion. This project seeks to avoid instrumentalization – or at least to create processes where what each partner gains is made a matter of curiosity, negotiation and genuinely reciprocal exchange amongst disciplinary equals. We will reflect on the development of Z-Time – from its conception through to the production of an artwork for a large art-science exhibition – and will share some practical lessons. We will consider the role of risk taking, institutional embeddedness, authorship, and the usefulness of threading the curatorial throughout the collaborative process. We suggest that treating purpose as a field of uncertainty rather than a preset goal is key in art-science collaborations, and that STS can both support and learn from the conversations that unfold in this more expansive ‘knowing space’ (Law 2017).

Session Organizer:

Hanna Rose Shell, University of Colorado Boulder

395. STS as a Critical Pedagogy Roundtable

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

In Summer 2021, the NSF-funded 'STS as a Critical Pedagogy Workshop' occurred over four separate online sessions, with approximately 35 participants primarily from the United States. The workshop's main goals were to cultivate community around STS pedagogies, and to interrogate what exactly STS might uniquely contribute to critical pedagogy interventions. Additionally, organizers were interested in examining how the boundaries between research, pedagogy, and engagement get made and unmade, hoping to make visible the practices that blur these boundaries or make it difficult to cross these boundaries. Imagining the workshop less as an event and more as a collaborative formation, participants were invited to coalesce into working groups around shared themes, and to collaboratively develop a panel session. These themes were broadly construed, drawing from participants' initial proposals, and initially framed as: "Feminist & Postcolonial STS / STS Laboratories, Clinics, and Data"; "Critical Play and Pop Culture"; "STS in STEM"; "Interrogating STS Pedagogies"; "Where is STS and STS Pedagogy?"; and "Medicine / Care / Disability." This roundtable will bring together participants from the workshop to discuss insights that emerged from it and to imagine the infrastructures and resources needed to further cultivate a community working on critical STS pedagogies.

Presenters:

Crystal Lee

Anna Geltzer, University of Notre Dame

Sean Ferguson, Engineering and Society, University of Virginia

Marisa R Brandt, Michigan State University

James Malazita, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Matthew Harsh, California Polytechnic State University

Matthew Wisnioski, Virginia Tech

Kathryn de Ridder-Vignone, South Carolina Governor's School for Science & Mathematics

Lindsay Adams Smith, Arizona State University

Session Organizer:

Emily York, James Madison University

Chair:

Shannon N. Conley, James Madison University

396. Challenges of -and Opportunities for- STS Undergraduate Programs, Teaching and Education - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Whether one characterises STS as an interdisciplinary field of inquiry, a full-fledge discipline, or otherwise, it is a body of knowledges and academic practices with its own core ideas, concepts, texts, journals, and professional associations. Yet education in STS is much less standardized than in other established fields and disciplines. While STS graduate programs exist in various forms and under various titles almost globally, undergraduate programs are much less common. Furthermore, given their interdisciplinarity, STS undergraduate programs face distinct sets of pedagogical and institutional challenges in terms of getting them established, as well as operating and maintaining them. At the same time, STS undergraduate programs are uniquely positioned to offer students with aspirations both within and outside the field, a set of theories, practices and methods that equip them to understand and address problems of inequality and uncertainty within our communities, institutions, and world. We invite papers that reflect on the pedagogical and institutional dynamics of teaching STS and developing STS programs at the undergraduate level. Submissions can be connected -but are not limited- to: •Undergraduate awareness of and general visibility of STS as a field •Impacts of disciplinary dynamics within STS on education and programing •Interdisciplinary education •Relationships with natural science programs, students, and faculty (i.e. Science Wars in education, the place of STS in mainstream STEM education) •Program development: majors, minors, core courses and electives •Institutional dynamics of program development •Appropriate modes of assessment •Researching STS pedagogy •Teaching the STS canon – best practices Potential topics include: STS undergraduate teaching, pedagogy, STS disciplinary development Jill Lazenby, York University, Toronto Conor Douglas, York University Vera Pavri, York University

Participants:

Experiential Learning as a Bridge to STS Theory in a Prerequisite STS Course *Jill Lazenby, York University, Toronto*

York University's STS undergraduate major and minor degree programs feature a required introductory course - "Introduction to Science and Technology Studies." This course provides a foundation for upper year STS courses, and is also taken as an elective by students who are interested in critically reflecting on science, technology and society. The course typically attracts a multidisciplinary group of students from the humanities and social sciences, as well as the STEM disciplines. Past instructors for "Intro to STS" have noted that despite the extensive discussion of STS history, theory and key case studies, some students experience a persistent difficulty in applying foundational STS perspectives. While these students may be able to describe STS theories and case studies on tests, their overall course work suggests that they maintain uncritical beliefs

in a single scientific method, in the dependence of technology on pure science alone, in the deficit model of the public understanding of science, and in the separation of science and the social. As a remedy, a prerequisite course is in development. This paper presents the course structure, along with sample experiential exercises and reflective assignments that are designed to act as a bridge to the more theoretical learning in "Intro to STS" and other STS courses.

Pedagogies of Practice and the Epistemic Capacities of Making
Kristen Lemma, Brown University

Taking as its premise that attention to practice and labor is crucial to understanding relations of power and knowledge production, this paper will explore the exercise of 'pedagogies of practice', or pedagogical processes that treat practice as central rather than ancillary to their execution. Much STS scholarship has been dedicated to inquiries into diverse forms of knowledge production, including the epistemic capacities of embodiment and practice. This author contends that it is essential to not merely read scholarship about the importance of practice, but to center the expertise of practitioners themselves and to actively engage in processes of making. This paper will take as its case study a course taught by the author at Brown University that heavily featured in-person and virtual interviews with information workers, as well as involved applied archival practice by students. Both of these direct forms of engagement with 'practice' radically altered our understandings of the theoretical scholarship that accompanied these experiences. This course's emphasis on the epistemic power of archival technologies was rendered material for students through a direct engagement with information workers, whose insights into the ethical, material, historiographic, and mnemonic dimensions of archival practice were invaluable. Centering the perspectives of practitioners allowed students to think theory alongside practice, while participating in archival labor allowed students to live theory alongside practice. This paper will articulate the ways that pedagogies of practice have an essential role to play in challenging conceptions of expertise, reimagining scholarship, and in further democratizing STS as a field.

STS Pedagogies In Higher Education Teacher Development: An Interdisciplinary Proposal From IT, Design And Law
Magda Pischetola, IT University Copenhagen

In-service higher education (HE) teachers face increasing challenges concerning the presence of digital technologies in teaching, as they need to expand their knowledge and competencies constantly and experience complex shifts in their professional identities. However, teacher professional development is often focused on educational technologies (e.g. tools and platforms) and it does not enable reflection on how production of academic knowledge is entangled with everyday pedagogical experiences, ways of being and doing. In this paper, we present a course-concept for HE teachers' professional development which attempts to address STS issues such as the profound intertwinement between technology and society and the mutual configuration of multiple knowledges and practices. The project, named Teknosofikum, is funded by the Danish Ministry of Higher Education and Science and developed collaboratively by four Danish institutions: IT University of Copenhagen, Royal Danish Academy of Architecture, Design and Conservation, University of Copenhagen – Faculty of Law, and Design School Kolding, between 2020 and 2023. Through a design-based research methodology in three iterations, Teknosofikum presents cases and scenarios from the disciplinary fields of Design, Information Technology and Law, with the aim to make them relevant for other academic fields. In this paper, we draw on data from the project first iteration, including curriculum design, prototype content development, and first trial with 45 course participants from the four institutions. A critical relational pedagogy is used as a frame for the learning activities design, based on the tradition of critical theory and the relational

perspectives informed by STS and sociomaterial feminist studies.

Session Organizers:

Conor Douglas, York University
Jill Lazenby, York University, Toronto
Vera Pavri, York University

Chair:

Conor Douglas, York University

Discussant:

Vera Pavri, York University

397. The Race to Digitalization and its attendant consequence of inequality - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

The global economy is experiencing increased digital transformation with its impacts felt globally and in all economic sectors. Digitalization enhances productivity with increased impacts on e-governance, telemedicine, distant learning, market access, remote-working, manufacturing etc. Digital technological capabilities however, remain concentrated in technological advanced economies and the digital economy is creating emerging new forms of inequality and wider technological gaps. The rise in digitization has reshaped markets, the world of business and work, raising inequalities within economies and distorting income distribution. The distribution of both capital and labor income has become more unequal, with income largely shifting from labor to capital. Developing countries (especially those in African) will not easily finance digitalization due to the high cost of infrastructure to develop and support robotics, automation and other digital technologies. The disruptions caused by COVID-19 pandemic have increased the need for digitalization and catch-up remains unattainable. New forms of nationalisms are growing, border closures and restrictions of movements of humans and goods are all in a bid to stop the spread of the virus. Digitalization is sure to increase if business transactions are to continue. This has made countries to develop national digital policies. However, policy failures of past industrial policies may still hunt these countries. This panel will contribute to knowledge on how to structure digitalization that will enhance the attainment of sustainable development to reduce inequality and technological divide. We are also seeking to understand the likely factors causing the digital divide and national policies to regulate the impacts digitalization in developing countries. Potential topics include: Digitalization, digital technologies, inequalities, developing countries, digital policies

Participants:

Digital Divide in Education in China during the COVID-19:
Factors and Policies
Yiran Gao, University of Illinois Urbana-Champaign

Since the start of the COVID pandemic, schools had been transited online in China to prevent physical mass gathering. This sudden transition faced unprecedented challenges in Midwestern China and rural areas due to the underdeveloped digital infrastructures in the regions and at homes, in contrast to the smoother transition in Eastern China and the urban areas. There is a significant gap in the digital infrastructures and online school skills and supports between teachers and students in different areas. Consequently, the online teaching and learning experiences for teachers and students in Midwestern and rural China were far from ideal during the quarantine. Under these circumstances, digitalization had not reduced inequity in education at a time of crisis but enlarged the country's education gaps. Looking at recent survey results on the digital infrastructures and home devices concerning online teaching and learning effectivity in different areas provided by several national research institutions, this paper first seeks to understand the political, economic, social, and cultural factors causing the digital divide in education. Furthermore, this paper reviews the policies the national and regional governments made in recent years regarding the construction of digital infrastructure and education to better understand the causes and impacts of the digital divide.

The Railway As A Transformative Actor: The "Deutsche Bahn"
Amid The Ecological And Digital Transitions And Public
Criticism *Stefan Laser, Siegen University*

This article is dedicated to the infrastructure politics of the "Deutsche Bahn", Europe's largest railway company. The basis of the discussion is ethnographic research and document analyses carried out in the Collaborative Research Centre "Media of Cooperation" (Siegen) in the sub-project "Structure and Change of Public Service Infrastructures." The project discusses the plurality of and uncertainty in dealing with the responsibility for maintaining and developing the railway infrastructure. Deutsche Bahn has long been subject to public criticism due to customer dissatisfaction and systematic overloads. With a new strategy and guided by political programmes, the organisation wants to propel and justify its restructuring. The article develops the argument that the railway is positioning itself as a transformative actor and is also called upon as such. With its "strong rail" programme (Starke Schiene), Deutsche Bahn explicitly addresses ecological and digital transformations. Covid has reiterated that goal. Do such new governance strategies also translate into new practices and relations of valuation; and what changes for involved actors? How do customers, engineers, but also different associations (such as trade unions and ecological movements) reflect on and co-shape these setups? The paper thus contributes to foundational matters of valuation studies: the question of collective attribution and allocation of responsibility in the context of complex collective valuation constellations. In general, the mobility transition is a "hot", i.e. still controversial, topic that is instructive for understanding public engagement. The analysis looks at both analogue and digital valuation practices to unfold the troubles at stake.

Remote Working and rise in today's inequalities *Emmanuel Ejim-Eze, Institute of Engineering, technology and innovation Management*

Remote work has been enabled by the rise in digitalization and diffusion of ICT technologies. COVID-19 has also emphasized the need for remote work to reduce human to human interactions and maintain social distance measures adopted by several countries. Whereas some countries allowed some levels of social activities to go on during the covid-19 lock downs, others shut down their economies in a bid to curtail the spread of the pandemic. However, opportunities only meet ready minds. Countries with good internet connectivity and other ICT infrastructure were able to transit to remote work or work from home. . The possibility of remote work for most jobs rests largely on internet access and this is limited in developing countries (World Bank, 2016). Others who were not ready simply shut down. This paper is looking out how remote work is increasing inequality in countries where people cannot work from home or where there are less remote work opportunities. Remote work today stands to widen the inequality gaps, as more men work from home, remote work is more in urban cities than in the rural areas and more rampant in developed countries than in developing countries. There are less jobs that require remote working compared to majority of jobs. More employees were laid with no option of remote working during the peak of the covid-19 pandemic This papers seeks to propose measures that can help policy makers and other stakeholders to develop the future work that will help accommodate remote working

Session Organizer:

Emmanuel Ejim-Eze, Institute of Engineering, technology and innovation Management

398. Thinking the Limits: AI Ethics/AI Unbound I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

In what way might it be productively disruptive to think through the "limits" of AI. Implicitly, we find in the call for an ethical AI or an

unbiased or fair AI a condition of a limit. Advanced automation may have a place in a post-industrial military-industrial complex, but that should not be the in the form of a military "killer robot." Algorithmic sorting can effectively produce types and categories, but that sorting should not reproduce a racist logic. And yet, the empirical difficulty of distinguishing the method and trajectory of the automated outcome—the black box state of current deep learning—broadly impacts the application of AI technology from the quotidian to the exceptional event. This panel discusses the idea of a "limit" to AI across several critical paradigms, including a feminist/queer technoscience ethical right of refusal, a critical race theory framing of eugenic programming and unbounded fugitive technologies, as well as geolocational political economies of AI industry including labor and environment.

Participants:

Racial Categories in Algorithmic Fairness Frameworks *Emily Denton, Google*

We examine the way race and racial categories are adopted in algorithmic fairness frameworks. Current methodologies fail to adequately account for the socially constructed nature of race, instead adopting a conceptualization of race as a fixed attribute. Treating race as an attribute, rather than a structural, institutional, and relational phenomenon, can serve to minimize the structural aspects of algorithmic unfairness. In this work, we focus on the history of racial categories and turn to critical race theory and sociological work on race and ethnicity to ground conceptualizations of race for fairness research, drawing on lessons from public health, biomedical research, and social survey research. We argue that algorithmic fairness researchers need to take into account the multidimensionality of race, take seriously the processes of conceptualizing and operationalizing race, focus on social processes which produce racial inequality, and consider perspectives of those most affected by sociotechnical systems.

Technology of the Surround: Generative AI *Beth Coleman, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto*

The focus of this paper is to articulate the concept of a technology of the surround, following the concept of the surround as developed by Harney and Moten. In addressing such, it also asks, what is the change of state a technology of the surround signals in relation to artificial intelligence (AI) frameworks and production in the recently seeded climate of machine learning and neural networks. Addressing critical frameworks established by Barad and Parisi, my argument is to make AI more wild, not less. I ask how might we consider a generative collusion, an itinerant alien intelligence to "think" through things differently than "we" might? In thinking the surround, this line of enquiry additionally asks if there is a relation between the historical subject unmoored, following a discourse of the subject unbounded. Even though there are other portals from which to enter, in this case the focus is on the pathological insistence on racial categories in Western hegemony that produces an automation of sorting race, place, things, etc. Along these lines, the argument addresses intersecting questions in regard to artificial intelligence, particularly focusing on the formal methods that distinguish structured from unstructured learning in relation to a prescriptive predictive paradigm that reinforces a eugenic sorting in comparison to an exploratory generative frame that offers possibilities of other thinking.

Thinking the Limits of AI to Break the Frames that Bind Us *Lucy Suchman, Lancaster University, UK*

This talk thinks through the limits of AI to disrupt that figure's expanding control over technopolitical discourses and agendas. I take 'AI' to reference a range of technologies of data processing and analysis based on the iterative adjustment of relevant parameters, according to some combination of internally and externally generated feedback. Efforts to contest the contribution of these technologies to the reproduction of bad relations (of white supremacy, incarceration, etc.) are threatened by a growing

industry traveling under the sign of AI ethics. I take as exemplars recent initiatives launched in the name of US national security, specifically the operations of the Defense Innovation Board and National Security Commission on AI. I trace the ways in which for both of these bodies 'AI' is framed as an autonomous actant demanding massive investment, while 'ethics' works as a device for the containment of more fundamental questions of law, politics, morality, and social justice. I close with some thoughts on lines of solidarity that can help us to unbind those questions.

Session Organizer:

Beth Coleman, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Meredith Broussard, associate professor at the Arthur L. Carter Journalism Institute of New York University

399. Agrifood Futures in-the-Making: Part IV

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

With a booming agritech sector, venture capitalists, philanthropists, scientists and engineers are playing an increasingly central role in shaping agrifood futures, both through the deployment of socio-technical imaginaries and the transformation of material realities. As a result, agrifood scholars are engaging with novel technologies including synthetic biology, tissue engineering, digitization, robotics, artificial intelligence and related fields. Scholarship at the intersection of STS and agrifood studies allows for critical examination of the tensions between agritech's aspirations to radically transform farming and food systems, and the profound ecological and social consequences these transformations might entail. Papers in these four panels offer critical insights into contested agrifood futures in-the-making. Panels I and II will explore what it means to engineer both the 'perfect farm' and the 'perfect food.' Panels III and IV will discuss contested ideologies and ontologies of food, agriculture and technology. These panels highlight the work of scholars affiliated with the STS Food & Agriculture Network (STSFAN), a small but growing intellectual community. We also invite anyone interested in our work to join our conference Meetup to learn more about the network.

Participants:

What is a food system? An analysis of competing transformative visions *Samara Brock, Yale University*
STS has long engaged with complex systems thinking. Scholars drawing from post-humanism, phenomenology, Actor-Network Theory, indigenous ontologies, and an array of other relational/ecological approaches have highlighted "unruly assemblages" that enable the discipline to work against tidy simplifications (Fletcher and Clarke 2018). With increasing mobilization of the food systems frame, as signaled by the first ever UN-sponsored global food systems summit in 2021, what insights might STS' engagement with systems bring to thinking through and enacting "the food system?" Much food scholarship has focused on food systems without analyzing in-depth what a system is, how the term came to be widely accepted, and what its use accomplishes. Pulling from ethnographic research with influential transnational organizations engaged in global food system transformation, this paper brings STS' engagement with systems towards a new analysis of systems in practice in the agrifood context. It builds conceptually upon Dupuis' (2013) fermentive politics, Paxson's (2013) microbiopolitics, and Mol's (1999) ontological politics to explore both the managerial and relational politics that emerge through leveraging the concept. In turn, the paper asks how food systems work in this material, trans-national, and transformative context can inform STS' further engagement with systems approaches.

Farm Ontologies: From Plots to Pixels *Emily Reisman, University at Buffalo*

Farms have long been a site of ontological tension and multiplicity. A farm can be a legal relationship to land, a foil to wilderness, a governable and taxable unit, an obligation of care, a foundation of civic engagement, a biological factory and more.

There is nothing natural about what a farm is; the farm is always in the making. In this paper I consider how emerging agricultural technologies are shifting the ontological horizon of the farm and explore what implications such shifts may carry. This analysis draws on over 2 years of collaborative fieldwork in the Silicon Valley Agri-food Technology sector with the California AFTeR Project. Previous studies emphasize productivist conceptualizations of farms as factories, defined by inputs and outputs, but digital technologies unsettle the materiality of the farm itself. This paper mobilizes STS and agrarian political economy to examine the stakes of ontological politics for the future of farming. How might the ontological status of the farm change when its "digital twin" is more readily engaged with than the land itself? Can a farm be a dataset? Are bioreactors farms? Can farms exist independent of land? Digitized agricultural endeavors rely quite literally on creating and stabilizing computational ontologies which define and structure a farm's transubstantiation into information. Why does this matter? While the shifting ontological terrain of farming may not be new, its contours carry implications for whose actions are validated or invalidated, how policy interventions are structured, and the blind spots that are produced and reinforced.

What is a plant? Constructing robot ontologies through sensors and code *Karly Burch, University of Otago; Katharine Legun, Wageningen University*

Robotics with artificial intelligence capacities are currently being developed for complex tasks in agriculture, although many are at an experimental stage and have yet to reach commercial viability. At this early development stage, the design of technologies can be seen at their most elemental stage, where they set the infrastructure for potential sophisticated iterations of AgTech in the future. Drawing from interviews with engineers and computer scientists on a large co-design project, this paper will explore the translation of complex agricultural tasks into AI robotics. We pay particular attention to the materialities of these technologies and the capacities they make possible—e.g., the abilities to construct sensation, to move, to make decisions, to learn. By attending to the components that go into developing robotics, and how engineers describe their abilities and networked interactions, we aim to better explicate how a robot can see, think, and act. While these robotics are often modeled from humans, they are fundamentally distinct. Better explicating robot ontologies can help us to clarify the social and environmental dynamics of their development, while also allowing us to tease apart the differences between the imaginaries and realities they produce.

Different Perspectives or Planets?: A case study of differing ontologies of agroecology and ag-tech *Summer Sullivan, UC Santa Cruz*

Two fields claim their practices can get us closer to a better farming future: agricultural-technology (ag-tech) and agroecology. Yet, it is unclear whether these approaches are compatible. Integrating Western science, indigenous knowledge, and social movements, agroecology is a place-based, ecosystemic farming approach. Ag-tech trends toward problem-solving, scalability, and efficiency, making farming quicker and less resource intensive. Preliminary research from a case study of a new initiative at the University of California, Santa Cruz (UCSC) to integrate the two fields provides novel insights and avenues to better understanding the nature of these differences. Interviews with an expected 20 UCSC project stakeholders, many of whom have an institutional commitment to find common ground, indicate not only differences in ideological and historical underpinnings, but starkly divergent epistemological and ontological grounds on which they approach this project. Prominent tensions include the site of intervention, notions of what is at stake, political economy, and understanding and role of both technology and social science. STS analyses of interdisciplinary conflict and related 'boundary work' tensions tend to focus on epistemological elements, and while I draw on

these insights, I suggest an ontological dimension of divergence that further troubles the nature of and potential for interdisciplinary science collaboration. Using a framework that engages the ontological turn in STS, particularly Hugh Campbell's interpretation of Annemarie Mol's multiple ontologies, I explore its pertinence to ag-tech at UCSC while considering the theoretical and material implications of ontological divergence alongside the real—though difficult to realize— synergistic potential between agroecology and ag-tech.

Session Organizer:

Mascha Gugganig, University of Ottawa

Discussant:

Charlie Mather, Department of Geography, Memorial University

400. Toward a Critical Health Informatics: Traversing Policy and Practice I - Concepts and Foundations

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This first session features works that centralize theoretical, conceptual, and foundational contributions to critical health informatics.

Participants:

Introducing critical health informatics *Mustafa Ibraheem*

Hussain, Oregon Health and Science University

While the 'critical health informatics' label is to the best of my knowledge novel, the concept has rich roots in STS, health informatics, and technology-oriented fields such as human-computer interaction and computer-supported cooperative work. The branches of critical health informatics reach toward policy, critically reinterpreting emergent questions and frameworks about technology, society, and health while providing theoretical nutrition to the fields at the root. In this talk, I will provide a brief overview of some foundational critical health informatics work, the monumental challenges and opportunities of the near-present, and the possible and preferable futures of health informatics in policy and practice. I will focus mainly on the role of STS scholars in the international effort to build bridges between neglected pasts, desperate presents, and preferable futures; between scholarly circles and those clinical professions which best serve working people, centralizing those perspectives which gather around the nexus of health information policy with the goals of placing the necessary restraints on power, rebuilding publics, and bringing to fruition the policy-idealized futures of healthy societies enabled by robust technological infrastructure that were all but brought to a halt in the early 1970s.

Governance by (data health) infrastructure: The case of immunity passports *Stefania Milan, University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands*

The response to COVID-19 is oversupplied with risk-reduction technical solutions, including thermal cameras and facial recognition tech, predictive analytics and contact tracing apps. The pandemic has accelerated the transition to governance by (health) data infrastructure, whereby data infrastructures has been elevated to the main mode of governance of complexity. These tools, often used for purposes other than what they were designed for, are leveraged by policymakers to support strategic decisions such as the imposition of curfews and lockdowns. But the pandemic has also fast-tracked the creation of consumer technology to offsets the social costs of the crisis—a new wave of critical health informatics solutions often adopted outside of any mechanism of democratic oversight. The vaguely formulated “immunity passports” are a case in point. They are expected to help restarting the economy, including travel, by attesting that a person has tested negative to the virus, or has been vaccinated or again has been infected and is now allegedly immune. This paper analyses the new kid in the block of interoperable health systems, namely the “immunity passport” project of the European Union,

nicknamed “Digital Green Certificate”, a “uniform” and “interoperable” certificate reporting the medical record of European citizens. The controversial project foresees the creation of a regional tracking and verification infrastructure, which requires—at the bare minimum—national health (including vaccination) and border databases be made interoperable and a process of standardization of the digital infrastructure. This speculative paper investigates the potential consequences of this standardization project on public health surveillance, human rights, and (dis)trust in public-sector data infrastructure.

Machine Work in Virtual Hospitals: Life Behind The Scenes in a Telemedicine Unit in Chile *Fernando Valenzuela, Universidad Andres Bello*

Implementing processes based on information and communication technologies produces profound transformations in health care systems. In the interface between the sociology of health and Science and Technology Studies, a growing literature has explored the challenges this entails for the organisations and actors involved, emphasising physicians, nurses, and patients' experience. Based on interviews and observations conducted in a telemedicine unit in Chile, this presentation seeks to contribute to the development of a critical understanding of medical informatics. Following the program of a sociology of the invisible, it analyses different facets of the work that technical support and coordination teams do behind the scenes and that makes telemedicine possible at this site. Five dimensions of their work are distinguished, which go beyond the mechanical kind of machine work that is evident at first glance: struggle, accommodate and influence in organisational networks; translate the logics of healthcare; transform and mobilise inscriptions; articulate tasks; and protect patients. Addressing these different dimensions allows bringing to light the complex intermingling of medical informatics in daily practices and the mechanisms that make it go mostly behind the scenes.

Synthesizing Neurobiological Lab Work with Clinical Practice in an ADHD Clinic *Andrew Ivan Brown, Social and Political Thought, York University*

Attention-Deficit/Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is widely accepted by the scientific-medical community as having a neurobiological basis. While much has been written in social science literature on how framings of the self have turned neurobiological in recent years (Rose and Abi-Rached 2013), less attention has been paid to the intersections of laboratory work on the brain and clinical practice. In this paper, I present an ethnographic case study of an English-speaking ADHD clinic located in Okinawa, Japan which identifies itself as a “research centre” but actually outsources its “lab work” (research into brain scan imagery of reward and punishment processes in ADHD children) to a Brazilian company. Using open-ended interviews and participant observation, I parse out how these clinicians in Okinawa understand their individual roles. To what extent do they seem themselves as cutting-edge researchers of the brain rather than strictly clinicians? How do they interpret their clinic's institutional relations (to the Brazilian lab; to the Okinawa Institute of Science and Technology which funds them; and to the Japanese government)? Further, does the clinic's emphasis on neurobiological research and its collaboration with the Brazilian lab actually influence clinical practice? In what sense is the clinic a “qualitative lab”? Finally, what power dynamics are in play between these various actors and institutions, and how do such dynamics ultimately attempt to legitimize ADHD in a country whose mental health systems have “lagged behind” Western biomedical systems, and where ADHD is still largely unknown to the broader public?

Session Organizer:

Mustafa Ibraheem Hussain, Oregon Health and Science University

Chair:

Kim M Unertl, Vanderbilt University Medical Center
Department of Biomedical Informatics

Discussant:

Mustafa Ibraheem Hussain, Oregon Health and Science
University

401. Uses, strategies and knowledge production in mobility contexts - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Participants:

Which institutional and theoretical frameworks for collective dimension of researches toward situations of compelled or impeded mobility? *Jöelle Le Marec, Université Paris Sorbonne; Brouard Pauline, Sorbonne Université*

We propose to discuss here a work in progress regarding the construction of a theoretical and institutional framework for multiple research situations, including collective ones, which jeopardize the dominant idea of international research construed as a system of coordinated activities and operations relating to project logics and anticipation (Graber, 2016). The framework of "knowledge from precarity" requires sharing the numerous situations of forced or impeded mobility, which can interrupt the course of research or careers (Duplessis and Le Marec, 2020, Broitman and Le Marec, in progress). On the one hand, we will start from the way of building international network that lead to the construction of theoretical frameworks enabling researchers to describe and share knowledge from forced or hindered mobilities, and, on the other hand, we will address specific situations, about direction of research or about doctoral research, which oblige us to reappropriate investigation trajectories through other temporalities than those of the thesis or programs. These situations experienced as obstacles at an institutional level are sometimes directly linked with the perspectives that we can open up thanks to a pragmatic approach to experience and by paying attention not only to what is developed in productions and discourses, but also to what is experienced in situations that seem to be parentheses, preliminaries, interruptions.

Epistemic disparities in times of uncertainty and vulnerability
Hester du Plessis, University of Pretoria

The 2020 coronavirus (Covid-19) pandemic with its global lockdown decisions exposed economic, social and political fault lines within the fabric of societies across the world. The socially disruptive lockdowns brought to light the punitive price humanity is paying by promoting science with an exclusive focus on preserving human life above that of maintaining an ecologically balanced approach. It also brought to light the vulnerability of current socio-political systems, our dependence on technology and the growing challenges we face in our quest for new knowledge. Facing the threat of new viruses is not new. However, by unleashing the practice of Biopolitics, supported by the application of Biopower, politicians now control our health, invade our personal life-styles and close down most economically viable businesses and educational support systems. As a result, we have a society that academically faces limited personal contact for meaningful intellectual exchanges. Growing 'intellectual nomadism' is also transforming our opportunities for creating new knowledge by enabling us to work from remote localities. With societies facing disruptive events of uncertainty and vulnerability, this paper will query whether the lack of personal contact is creating epistemic disparities in the traditionally rich way we create, disseminate and manage the knowledge that is generated inside and outside of institutional environments and academic regulations. I will try to establish whether social isolation, as well as the growing evidence of our new 'intellectual migration' opportunities, provides the necessary opportunity to facilitate epistemic growth.

Mobility: What For? The Worst Side of a Bad Idea *Javier López Alós*

This proposal seeks to examine the relation between the impact of academic mobility on the researchers' subjective experiences and its consequences on the ultimate knowledge production. The initial hypothesis is that, in contrast to the neoliberal university dominant discourse, the current paradigm of mobility is not only detrimental to the subjects, but also to the resulting scientific objects or output. Ruled by principles of performance maximization, financial efficiency and competitiveness, notions such as exchange, community and collegiality seem to face a gloomier future than opportunism and temporary jobs. Related to precariousness, the term mobility has turned into a successful euphemism for exodus, exile and intellectual nomadism. Moreover, understood as a merit, it works as an obligatory requirement for any academic career development, a necessary condition. In this context, mobility means more than the ability to move or be moved. Amidst this constant movement, mobility also implies or demands the capacity of the individuals to resist without their professional careers dissolving along the way. In addition, the relationship of mobility as a merit and precariousness is two-sided: it is a result, as well as an intensifier. That is, with no other option but to keep moving, the precariousness of the nomad may become an obstacle for the so celebrated mobility itself, turning into another factor for increasing inequality.

Morocco in the mirror of migrations *Kenza Sefrioui, EN TOUTES LETTRES*

Since the 2000s, Morocco, a country of departure and transit, also became a host country, due to the policies of closing European Union's external borders. Migrants represent a tiny part (0.25%) of the population, but the approach of the subject in the public debate reflects the divisions of Moroccan society. A large part of the press focuses on the migrants coming from sub-Saharan Africa, though they are a minority. The same press doesn't consider Europeans as migrants but as "expatriates": this analysis bears the traces of the history of slavery, of colonial history, and of their racist hierarchies. On the opposite of these speeches, civil society, mainly the human rights movement, thinks the situation of the migrants as an opportunity to reformulate the demand for the democratization of the country. Freedom of conscience, of worship, individual freedoms, transparency of institutions, accountability, social justice, etc., the advocacy focuses on the issues which deficit is the main cause of departure of young Moroccans (brain drain as illegal immigration). The migration issues raise one again the lack of a full citizenship for both Moroccans and migrants. This action pushed Morocco to adopt a National Immigration and Asylum Strategy in 2014 and regularize 50,000 migrants, which made it the only country in the Southern Mediterranean to do so. But the process remains unfinished. Such crucial issues need to be documented through serious investigations by journalists and researchers in human and social sciences. Publishers also have to take their responsibility in order to spread informations.

Scientific Elites in Developing Countries: the case of Colombia
Julian David Cortes Sanchez, School of Management, Universidad del Rosario

Research conducted by scientific elites (SE) pushes the frontiers of knowledge. However, studies on SE's acknowledged by important awards or a cumulative advantage have focused mainly on developed countries. For instance, Nobel awardees or to be ranked among the most cited researchers worldwide. That leaves a substantial gap for understanding SE's nature according to developing countries' historical, economic, institutional, cultural contexts and research standards. This study focuses on Colombia's SE (CSE). Compared to global SE yardsticks, only two Colombians have been awarded the Nobel Prize --none of them in science. And, only one researcher figures among the

most cited researchers worldwide. Yet, in the Latin-American context, Colombia figures among the top five countries in research output and the top fifty in total citations worldwide (1996-2019). Also, Colombia has its own "Nobel Prize" granted by the Alejandro Ángel Escobar Foundation --whose founder was inspired by the Swedish inventor and his legacy. Here, we explore the CSE demographics, scientific collaboration, and research topics' structure. We will use science mapping techniques, such as keyword co-occurrences and co-authorship networks. Our main contribution to STS relies upon two grounds: i) understanding developing countries' SE demographics, local/global collaboration and main research topics; and ii) disentangling the research performance and research agenda between the North-South, looking at a context-nested examination.

Session Organizer:

Patricia Rivero, Universidad de Córdoba

Chair:

Jöelle Le Marec, Université Paris Sorbonne

Discussant:

Claudio Broitman Rojas, Universidad Andrés Bello

402. Viral Relationalities I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

These are unprecedented times, or so we are told through COVID-19 communications articulated by global health institutions and national governments. Such exceptionalism foregrounds the significance of the current crisis – its bodily and economic impacts, the global and local inequities that have materialized and the myriad meanings it has created. Yet this exceptionalism, in practices and discourses, also gives rise to hierarchies of knowledge production. Ontologies and epistemologies advanced by global and national health responses construe the virus as a discrete, measurable entity. Such dominant framing might connect COVID-19 with other epidemics, as for instance HIV, but disarticulates the viral from local marginalized knowledges and modes of worlding. Consequently, borders are erected - geopolitically, between bodies and knowledge generating disciplines, temporalities, and across socio-economic differences - in the name of exceptionalism. What queer, Indigenous, and decolonial knowledges, histories, embodied effects and meanings can be highlighted if we understand that COVID-19 and other epidemics are exceptional through the particular relations they put in place or displace? This panel doesn't dismiss COVID-19's local and global significance, but instead invites contributors to inhabit virality's exceptionalism in relational terms: querying science's entanglements with politics; reconceiving intimacies and viral transmission; positing other temporalities and post-COVID futurity narratives. Papers in this Session together with its companion Session, Viral Relationalities II consider: - viruses' entanglements with pre-existing states of perpetual crisis - practices of survivance and imaginings of futurities as lived by ethnic, racial, sexual and gender minorities - other means of embodying post-colonial/settler colonial realities in the viral present

Participants:

PrEP and gay men's experiences of AIDS cultural memory
Benjamin Riley, Department of Gender and Cultural Studies,
University of Sydney

Gay men have been tied to AIDS since the beginning of the epidemic—epidemiologically, historically and psychically. While narratives describing that relationship have shifted over the past four decades, its legacy has endured in gay male bodies as a fear of becoming HIV-positive. Discussions of "HIV anxiety" abound in recent STS scholarship around pre-exposure prophylaxis for HIV (PrEP), which suggest PrEP can reduce or even eliminate this anxiety (e.g. Calabrese & Underhill 2015; Hojilla et al. 2016; Prestage et al. 2019). However, little research has aimed to link PrEP use to gay men's embodied experiences of the legacy of AIDS. This paper will explore those under-examined links by explicitly framing HIV anxiety as an example

of gay men's embodied experiences of AIDS cultural memory. The paper will argue that by reducing HIV anxiety, PrEP may serve to re-frame gay men's relationship not only to HIV, but to how they situate themselves within larger cultural narratives of AIDS and gay experience. It will suggest that by enabling gay men to reimagine their relationship to AIDS history, PrEP might create space for new ways of imagining gay futures. This paper is part of a study interviewing gay and other same-sex attracted men about their experiences using PrEP as a HIV-prevention method. The study focuses on the impact of PrEP use on gay men's understanding of themselves within larger cultural narratives of AIDS and gay experience.

Viral Entanglements: Pig-Human Relations and the Limits of Viral and Human Exceptionalism in India
Shweta Krishnan, George Washington University

How do you mourn pigs in the midst of a global pandemic that is claiming human lives? In April 2020, in the face of a nation-wide lockdown in relation to the corona pandemic, a large number of migrant workers from Mising tribal villages in the Indian state of Assam found themselves stranded in other parts of the country. In the following days, they were among those migrant workers in India, who began to walk back home in the hottest summer months. Even as parents of these migrant workers worried about their safe return, an epidemic of African Swine Flu swept across the state, killing the pigs that were being raised in Mising homes. Studying the entangled and overlapping temporalities of both infections, this paper asks what it means to grieve the loss of pigs and the precarity of human lives side by side. Demonstrating how pig-human relations are already significant in these communities, and how these kinships (Haraway 2008, Govindarajan 2019) already position the tribe within a "savage slot," (Trouillot 2003) in a Hindu nationalist state, this paper examines how the circulation of two viruses complicates an already precarious and racialized relationship between humans and nonhumans. I argue that Mising attentiveness to pigs not only questions the limits of the exceptionalism vis-à-vis the pandemic, but also the limits of human exceptionalism that shapes the responses of postcolonial states.

Stigma in Pastpresent Times
Annette-Carina van der Zaag, Birkbeck; Annette-Carina van der Zaag, Birkbeck, University of London

This paper sets out a theoretical contemplation on stigma to explore the manner in which pastpresents of HIV come into view through the current coronavirus crisis. In particular the paper seeks to expand an understanding of stigma beyond Goffman's 'spoiled identity' and thus beyond stigmatization as lived cultural economy of marginalization. Rather, this paper articulates stigma through a material/ist scope, by bringing into conversation black studies articulations of violence, racialization and time following Hortense Spillers and Karen Barad's posthuman theorization of materiality, temporality and justice. Here the paper takes particular inspiration from Hortense Spillers' hieroglyphics of the flesh, those stigmatizing marks through which (post-)slavery subjects emerge, in order to contemplate stigma as a substantiation of time that speaks traces of the past while dis/articulating the break towards an elsewhere to come. And takes inspiration from Karen Barad and their notion of spacetime-mattering to articulate the continuity of stigmatization across a nonlinear pastpresent material trajectory. The paper argues that such theoretical contemplations are vital to the material temporality of Covid-19, the marks (to be) left in its wake and the manner in which these speak histories of virality that are in no sense unprecedented. As such, this paper contributes to STS by elaborating a decolonial engagement with materiality and time facilitated by a meeting of neomaterialism and black studies, a conversation invoked by coronavirus as a nonhuman agent with whom we must learn to converse.

Viral Knowledge
Paul Boyce, University of Sussex

This paper explores the relational attributes of viral knowledge. In pursuing this perspective I trace connections and fissures between HIV prevention research actions, responses to COVID 19, and sexual life-worlds – in the context of India. My aim, however, is not to simply track such interactions as information flows or end-points between people and health promotion knowledge. Rather I am interested in ways in which sexualness has been conceived in research and interventions recursively with ways in which sexual-worldings have shaped the production of knowledge about the epidemics to hand. There are no wholly extant, prefigured sexual subjects waiting in the world for the interpretive actions of researchers in these terms. And nor are methods of viral knowledge making extant – separate from the sexual. Rather sexual subjectivities and the production of knowledge about viral entities emerge as coeval; partial processes ‘on-goingly’ re-figuring and reconstituting the other across sites and interactions. Knowledge is conceived accordingly as a series of shifting ‘merographic’ connections and ellipses that both reveal and obscure viral relationalities.

Session Organizers:

Rory D Crath, Smith College

Annette-Carina van der Zaag, Birkbeck, University of London

Paul Boyce, University of Sussex

403. Canadian Science = Settler Science - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

This session explores the multitude of ways that colonial, settler science in Canada masquerades as democratic, and how some Indigenous and non-Indigenous actors are unsettling what counts as ‘Canadian’ science. Technoscientific institutions and practices are a primary modality through which the settler colonial state inflicts violence, and this violence is enacted both materially and epistemically. We suggest that technoscientific practice—be it microbiology, genomics, demography, fisheries, mining, forestry, or data science and AI—continues to do the work of the contemporary colonial state in Canada by reinforcing colonial hierarchies and exclusion, legitimating capitalist extraction, propping up liberal ideas of multiculturalism and diversity, and enabling cultural genocide. This panel also addresses Canadian scientific and innovation infrastructure—tri-council funding agencies and academic and federal science—to consider how funding and research structures enable the ongoing exclusion and marginalization of Indigenous knowledges and practices. We invite contributions from scholars exploring a range of technoscientific practices, actors, and areas of expertise in the Canadian context to examine the national politics of transnational technoscience in the settler state. How has settler science worked to delegitimize Indigenous-led projects? How can we remake technoscientific methods in order to move toward caring, good relations? We seek papers that offer empirically grounded analyses of the relations and material practices that make up settler science. By examining the ways in which Canadian technoscience might be unsettled and decolonized, we aim to facilitate urgently-needed conversations in STS on the possibilities for challenging the persistent colonial work of Canadian scientific projects.

Participants:

Settler science, biogovernance, and the politics of care in Vancouver’s Unceded Territory *Denielle a Elliott*, *York University*

In the 1990s, multiple levels of the Canadian state assembled a complex web of technoscientific interventions aimed at addressing dual localized epidemics of HIV/AIDS and addictions in Vancouver’s Downtown Eastside (DTES). Bioscientific institutions merged with socio-economic service provision including housing and income assistance, as they took over and reconfigured the DTES landscape, remaking the community into an urban laboratory. As part of this, the settler state needed to reinvent itself as a caring, beneficent state who was concerned with the wellbeing and health of its urban, disproportionately Indigenous, residents. I argue here that underlying its framing as

a liberal, caring response, the entire machinery was predicated on settler colonial logics about indigeneity and disposable citizens. Drawn from ethnographic fieldwork, this paper explores the tension as a settler state adopts an affective register to care for those they have abandoned. I consider how the state and its agents developed new technoscientific interventions that lured urban peoples into ‘caring’ structures that were largely a mode of control through biology and bodies. DTES residents were entangled in this technoscience web through pharmaceuticals, DNA tracing, experimental medicine, and epidemiological surveillance. While many ‘refused’ or resisted this machinery, others chose to be ‘cared for’ by the state even in its most controlling and violent form because the alternative for many would have been abandonment or death. I illustrate how complicated the politics of refusal, resistance, and acceptance was for urban poor residents as they navigated the ‘caring’ economy of the Canadian settler state.

Population Genetics at the Intersection of Settler Colonialism *Darryl Leroux*, *Saint Mary's University*

This paper examines the work of population genetics in furthering white settler colonialism in Canada. Over the course of the past two decades, a robust public-private national genomics sector has developed in the province of Québec. The sector builds on the unmatched genealogical records available for the French-descendant population of the region, spanning a period of about 400 years. Working with such an unmatched genealogical data source, population genetics has become de rigueur in labs across the province; a few key research teams have become global leaders in the study of the genetic superiority of white settlers on the frontier (“expanding wave front”), or of mapping the Indigenous origins of a European “founder population.” Just as population genetics has entered into mainstream parlance, a social movement has emerged whereby otherwise white French-descendants claim a newfound “Indigenous” identity that is counter to existing Indigenous understandings of governance, kinship, and citizenship. By analyzing several high-profile population genetics projects that intervene in complex settler-Indigenous relations, I consider how genetic scientists contribute to a movement that is widely regarded as a contemporary iteration of settler colonialism.

Reckoning: Risk Tools, Settler Science, and Carceral Drift *Michelle Stewart*, *University of Regina*

This paper proposes a reckoning. Tracing out the machinery of bureaucratic violence in the settler state, the paper will analyze risk management tools used to enhance carceral drift and displacement. Tools to measure, manage and mitigate perceived risk are emblematic of what Razack (2021) calls a “project of racial accumulation” that is predicated on the ongoing extraction of Indigenous lands and bodies. The paper will link these risk tools in justice settings to broader risk practices used in child welfare to demonstrate the profound ability of “best practices” to deliver settler displacement and accumulation. Drawing on the framing of “coded inequity” (Benjamin 2019), the paper will contribute to broader STS interventions that demonstrate the nuanced ways in which race/racism are erased as “objective” and “color-blind” tools displace critiques of structural inequality. This paper will also draw on the power of bracketing (Riles 2000) such that individuals can be reduced to scores and the contexts pushed to the margins—forgotten, scratched out, not relevant. Accordingly, the paper will investigate how risk tools can serve to mask settler “dis-ease” with regards to current rates of over-incarceration of Indigenous youth and adults. Settler colonial violence is bracketed out of discussions of incarceration as the always-already risky individual is presented as the project. Drawing on applied anthropological research and tool analysis in Canada, this paper will snap off the brackets to demonstrate how the violence of settler actuarial and bureaucratic tools are the foundation of racial accumulation in the settler state.

Retrospective Ethics and the Unsettled History of the

International Biological Program in Nunavut *Tess Lanzarotta, Northwestern University*

In May 2019, a group of Inuit from Igloodik, Nunavut, announced that they were suing the Canadian government. Five decades earlier, they had been involved in a series of disturbing experiments involving skin grafts, which had left them with visible scars. The Canadian scientists who had performed these experiments were working under the auspices of the Human Adaptability section of the International Biological Program (IBP), a “big science” initiative that ran from 1964-1974. The goal of the IBP was to explore how humans had adapted over time to the environmental and climatic conditions found in five distinct biomes. Inuit, who live in a climate that is often characterized by outcrops as “harsh” or “hostile,” had been targeted as a study population. Many IBP scientists, including those who experimented on Inuit, have discussed their research extensively—the program was far from covert—and have acknowledged that it would not meet contemporary ethical standards. However, they nonetheless generally insist that their work was harmless and met the standards of the time, even if it was “poorly understood” by the research subjects involved. This paper explores the history of the skin graft study and tracks subsequent efforts to situate it in within a narrative of biomedical and bioethical progress. In doing so, it provides a critique of bioethical concepts, like harm and informed consent, and explains why they are unable to adequately address the enduring forms of violence produced through settler colonial biological research.

Session Organizers:

Sarah Blacker, York University
Denielle a Elliott, York University

Chair:

Sarah Blacker, York University

404. Optical Media: The Impact of Visual Technologies - III

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Optical media, borrowed from Friedrich Kittler, is an expanded concept that connects photography, film and television with other techniques and technologies that mediate optics and vision (e.g. microscopes, telescopes, oscilloscopes, echocardiography, ad inf.). Normalized, expected and often desired, optical media shape how we perceive the reality that surrounds us, mediating our understanding and experience of our inter- and intra-relationships with ourselves, others, objects, and worlds. In so doing, they constitute power relationships that reify inequalities and uncertainties, the key themes of 4S 2021, rendering certain people, places, and things visible, invisible, or hypervisible. These issues have grown in importance in the wake of COVID-19 and social distancing, where optical media have become ubiquitous. This panel welcomes interdisciplinary research from STS and neighbouring fields that critically examine the role of these embedded and disruptive technologies in guiding our world views and relationships. By paying attention to the modes of seeing and looking that shape our perceptions, behaviours, and practices we can begin to better address their effects on other information systems including but not limited to the ones we work in, socialize in, and reside in. Questions we ask include how are modes of looking shaped by digital optical media? What potentials are there for visual manipulation, exploitation, or psychological vulnerabilities? What new possibilities for ways of thinking, interacting or organizing information do these technologies offer? Who and what is being rendered visible, invisible, or hypervisible and the power politics of optical media?

Participants:

Body, Image, Mirror: Optical Aesthetics of the Self in Augmented Home Fitness *Katherine Contess, Brown University*

Among the slew of new fitness devices cum media platforms that have been released over the past few years, Mirror stands apart for its emphasis on the user's own image. A riff on the mirrored

walls of a gym or ballet studio that allow one to control one's body through one's own image, this interactive exercise device is simultaneously a mirror in the traditional, ornamental sense, and an LCD screen—a means of streaming live, on-demand workout classes in the home. One dimension (visually further and larger) is the user's own reflection, while the other dimension (seemingly closer and superimposed over the user's body) includes the miniaturized body of the instructor, appearing to float unmoored in the empty mirror space. The instructor's form also operates as an ideal; he or she completes each exercise with a routinized perfection that the user can only hope to imitate. While we're familiar with technologies like Google Glass which augment the user's vision of the outside world, Mirror applies the digitally augmented gaze back on the user's own body—it offers both reflection of the self and a technical transcendence of this self in one image. This paper explores the new optical aesthetics of the self presented by technologies like Mirror: how does it liquidate a traditional image of the body-image as whole in favor of a body visualized as a “prosthetic god”—connected to an arsenal of digital tools amplifying its capacities.

Looking-Through and Looking-At Selective Optical Media to Determine Subjectivities *Paula Sanchez Nunez de Villavicencio, University of Toronto*

Optical media—as discussed by Friedrich Kittler among other Communications Scholars—is defined by its ability to select, store, process, and transmit visual images, thereby transforming our optical practices and our visual culture. Predominantly, optical media is considered as those technologies we look at, such as television, the camera obscura, film, paintings, pictures or advertisements (Williams, Kittler, Daston and Galison, McLuhan). Changing trajectories, this paper focuses instead on those optical technologies that we look through—eyeglasses, stereoscopes, and smart glasses—to determine their role in mediating our optical practices and processes of visibility by establishing standards and norms for ways of looking. By considering the role of these wearable optical technologies in producing real-time images for individual experiences by co-processing visual information, this paper looks to critically analyze how modes of looking are shaped by selective optical media, and their resultant effects on our inter- and intra-relationships with our environments. Placing this argument in dialogue with Laura Mulvey's seminal work on the male gaze, this paper considers how the act of looking through an optical technology subjectivizes not only the looked-upon, but also the viewer. When our perceptions of reality are modulated by the technologies we confront the world through, our relationships with objects, others, and ourselves are also molded or produced by these technologies. By critically looking at these selective optical media we can determine which objects, images, people and places they make visible, or invisible, and their power to subjectivize.

How Science Sees Itself on TV: Popular Reality-Based Programming and the Instrumentalization of Television *Ben Riggs, Northwestern University*

Friedrich Kittler privileges technology over text. While discussing television, he writes that “even media theorists do not sufficiently realize that perceptible and aesthetic properties are always only dependent variables of technical feasibility.” But what happens when television's “technical feasibility” IS the aesthetic content of the medium? Alternatively, what happens when popular science TV turns its technical gaze on itself? Recent science-related programs like MythBusters (Discovery Channel, 2003-2016) and Planet Earth (BBC, 2006, 2016) have achieved commercial success by mixing traditional forms of documentary TV with ever more spectacular visuals and sensational “real-life” stories. This aesthetic embrace of reality-based spectacle has synchronously led to a literal foregrounding of the television apparatus itself -- cameras, lenses, rigs, and so on -- within these televisual texts. This paper uses close readings

of representative scenes from *MythBusters* and *Planet Earth* to theorize popular science's self-reflexive image(s) of television, wherein television is treated as being like a scientific instrument. This includes outlining how references to the technical apparatus (e.g., "Let's look at the high-speed camera") are used to both preemptively refute accusations of manipulation or error in the televised image as well as strategically recast on-screen personalities as "experts" in reading televisual data. Bridging disciplines (STS and media theory), this paper then examines the cultural acceptance of images as "truthful" or "indexical" via a discussion of genre. "Science" and "reality TV" make parallel claims to truthfulness and indexicality, and science television offers a unique opportunity for investigating how, when, and why optical media might make itself perceptible.

Seven-segment Display Lie *Yandong Li, University of Washington*

Look around you. There are dozens of old and new display methods and technologies ubiquitously used in displaying information. Seven-segment display, the ones we see on microwave panels, calculators, train stations, and gas stations often used for showing the numerical value of time and prices, seems a technology belonged to yesterday. What is so appealing in these seven segments making them prevalent worldwide in the past and present? In this essay, firstly, I will dig into a history of information technology of the seven-segment structure, from Reusser's telegraph alphabet to F. W. Wood's "Illuminated Announcement and Display Signal", and investigate what makes us follow this tradition of segmented structure. Power exists in order to be seen. The standard structure of the Seven-segment display is set by westerners while the structure has been carefully appropriated in Indian and Burmese languages in order to maintain the visual order. Moreover, the emergence of energy-efficient display technologies such as Light-Emitting Diode (LED) and Liquid-Crystal Display (LCD) fueled the dispersion of seven-segment display since the 1960s. By diving into a history of LED and LCD and their entanglements with the seven-segment display, I attempt to reveal the myth in the problematic ideas of growth and development embedded in standardization and efficiency. Ultimately, I argue that the pursuit of standardization and efficiency serves to sustain the mode of power display.

Session Organizers:

Paula Sanchez Nunez de Villavicencio, University of Toronto
Alexander Monea, George Mason University

405. Nonhuman Phenomenology and Technoscientific Intersubjectivity - 3: Phenomenological Mis/alignments

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Participants:

Haunted topographies of failed infrastructures; the ghosts of Sidewalk Toronto *Gregoire Camille Antoine Benzakin, University of Toronto*

Building on the recent reprises of Souriau's relational philosophy (Latour & Stengers, 2009; Latour, 2013; Debaise & Wiame, 2015; Lapoujade 2017), this article investigates how the uncanny figure of the ghost can help us re-think the narratives of failed infrastructure projects as "partial, contingent and always incomplete outcomes" (Knox et al, 2015). This article suggests that to declare an infrastructure project dead retrospectively allocates and reifies identities, roles and functions. The label failed project implies a specific ordering of reality, in which the existence of a project is ultimately conflated with its concrete materialisation. This paper seeks to suspend the temptation of closure and explore how spectres, as liminal beings, disturb the distinction between Being and Nothingness. Ghosts, we argue, contribute to a conception of infrastructures as the coalescence of a plurality of modes of existence, for which reality cannot be

simply reduced to materiality. Focusing on the controversies surrounding Sidewalk Toronto, a smart neighbourhood project which was abandoned in May 2020, we use the figure of the ghost to recast the project's failure, and deploy an alternative narrative of Sidewalk Toronto as an unsettled trajectory. Good or bad, ghosts highlight the possibility of other stories, other worlds and other futures. To Science and Technology Studies, they offer methods of dramatisation that reframe what it means to inherit failed infrastructure projects, and urge us to invent more than human worlds, on the basis of what is already here but often unperceived, the latent virtualities in the cracks of our modern ground.

Scaling Precarity: The Material-Semiotic Practices of Ocean Acidification *Mariko Yoshida, Hiroshima University, Japan*

In the context of the climate crisis, seawater scaling reveals the precarity of the ocean. Yet scaling as a process of knowledge production in ocean science unavoidably allows us to overlook the representation of complicated local biophysical relationships by using universalized measurements. Based on observations I made with a team of marine physiologists who investigate the effects of ocean acidification on mollusks, this paper shows practices of knowledge production about ocean precarity in Japan. By describing human-nonhuman entanglements that emerge in ecological disturbances, I demonstrate relational contestation over the measurement of unevenly distributed biosocial vulnerabilities. The sometimes unexpected interactions of sessile organisms, measurement devices, and marine physiologists with mollusks show complex processes of encounter rather than stylized biophysical representations. Recognizing the material semiotics of ocean acidification, in which chemical compounds, biological organisms, hydrological and geomorphological parameters, and other "things" become entangled, allows us to go beyond scalable metrics to understand the Ocean as a precarious place.

Sensing the truth: The relation of humans, animals and technology in security settings *Larissa Fischer, RWTH Aachen University; Bettina Paul, Universität Hamburg; Torsten H Voigt, RWTH Aachen University*

In order to improve security, airport officials and security authorities increasingly turn to semi- or fully automated "truth verification" procedures. These screening procedures are designed to identify individuals with malicious intentions by measuring non-verbal psycho-physiological parameters. When we started to investigate these technological truth verification procedures as part of a larger ethnographic study, we discovered that non-human species – specifically sniffer dogs to detect explosives – are a vital part in this larger domain of non-human security procedures. These animals are considered to possess skills, abilities and senses that are superior to technological and human security screenings. In this paper, we analyze the human, non-human, technology interaction in truth verification processes. We extend Bijker and Pinch's notion of the "sociotechnical ensemble" and reflect upon the triad at play. Our paper discerns human expectations that are directed towards non-human actors in contrast to the performance of the non-human artifacts. Central to our argument is the question of how non-human species fit into these automation developments and what kind of distinct abilities (senses) they add to the envisioned socio-technical security field. Furthermore, how are they integrated into this larger framework of truth verification? The argument is based on participant observations, interviews, and document analyses.

The Desired Disobedience Of Sniffer Dogs: A Proposal For The Incorporation Of Actor-Network Theory Into Contemporary Artifact Analysis *Dana Bock; Nicolas Martin Kohl*

Contemporary artifact analysis and STS may have only scraped the surface when it comes to challenging the notion of agency as something that is exclusive to human animals. To further the understanding of interactions between human animals and non-

human animals, it does not suffice to describe non-human animals as mere artifacts produced to perform certain tasks. In no case is this as apparent as with sniffer dogs. Under scrutiny, the idea of sniffer dogs being just another type of human-produced artifact reveals its shortcomings due to what we call desired disobedience. During our field-research, we observed dogs frequently ignoring orders from their handlers, only to find the hidden target the handlers missed. The sniffer dog handlers themselves claimed that this was by design. However, we argue that it is manifestly absurd to claim that this disobedience can be purely human-made programming. On the contrary, it requires the sniffer dogs to actively decide to disobey orders and to go against the very programming human animals have intended them to function by. The data collected for this project stems from participant observations during two field accesses, as well as both narrative and guided interviews with sniffer dog handlers and leading personnel of two German federal sniffer dog schools. Furthermore, as this project opens up a theoretical debate, we follow the steps laid out by Froschauer and Lueger in their 2018 book *Artefaktanalyse* and offer a proposition on how to expand it using actor-network theory brought forth by Latour and Haraway.

The Ugliness of Multispecies Intersubjectivity: Pandemic Racism And The Love Of Animals In The UK *maythe han, The University of Edinburgh*

What kinds of narratives and discourses emerge and spread when a viral crisis and a racial crisis coincide? Who is considered ‘contagious’, by whom, and why? In this paper based on ongoing digital ethnographic fieldwork, I look at the strange and frightening intersection of the love of animals and the deeply entrenched racism toward Black people and people of colour endemic to Britain. My data come in the form of a meme and a long thread of comments in response to it. The meme depicts a protestor who is about to throw a brick at a police horse and calls for protestors throwing things at police animals to be shot, placing the pain of the horse above the life of a protestor. This meme made a brief appearance on a UK-based dog people’s group on Facebook before it got deleted by the person who originally posted it, so the comment thread only lives as a series of screenshots on my computer. I follow multiple conversations in the comment thread to elucidate how the discourse surrounding, as well as the public fear of, viral infection has been co-opted by white British people who self-identify as ‘animal lovers’ in order to justify their racist stance: the kind of people who would move mountains for the wellbeing of nonhuman animals while they remain shockingly callous toward the systemic violence aimed at the lives of racialized people. I then argue that portraying Black Lives Matter protesters as spreaders of COVID-19 in the time of life-or-death struggle against racialized police brutality is a form of strategic racism that is painfully yet also easily compatible with love, empathy, and intersubjective kinship they share with their beloved nonhuman animal.

Session Organizer:

Claire Isabel Webb, University of Southern California

Chair:

Richard Fadok, MIT

406. The Crisis of AI: Towards a New Paradigm II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

The European Commission has recently announced a bold proposal for regulating Artificial Intelligence through a risk-based approach, which combines prohibitions for certain types of AI practices, a clear and adaptable regulatory framework for high-risk applications, and voluntary codes of conduct for low risk uses of AI. Anyone who has followed the trajectory of EU legislative acts so far should be able to identify a clear shift from a debate centered on ethics in AI, to one centered on law and fundamental rights, where ethics seems to play an ancillary role. This paper

seeks to analyze the meaning of such transition as a means to shed light into a broader question, namely, how we, as a society, want to build our relationship with artificial intelligence. More specifically, I will attempt to answer the following question: what is the meaning and implications of the shift from ethics into law and fundamental rights in the governance of artificial intelligence in the EU? As complementary goals, I intend to determine what this transition can tell us about: (1) technology regulation, in general, and (2) the specific challenges faced by the attempts to define the boundaries between ethics, law and fundamental rights. The paper will rely mainly on science and technology studies, on the law & technology literature and on discussions on rights and bioethics. A thorough research in legal and policy documents related to the topic at stake will also be carried out.

Participants:

YouTube’s AI-based Policing of Misinformation in the Covid-19 Crisis *Brian Pleasants Harper, Indiana University Bloomington*

Social media platforms have gained a prominent role in spreading news and information in the Covid-19 crisis. While all media sources have been forced to contend with the spread of misinformation in this pandemic, social media platforms have varied in the speed and strength with which they combat misinformation and have often used the same tools to combat misinformation that they usually use: the AI-based algorithmic detection and deletion of problematic content. However, while this approach has certainly deleted many videos and may have diminished the effects of misinformation, it focuses excessively on the elements of the platform that these automated systems may most easily police while avoiding the others. This paper seeks to provide an overview of the use and consequences of these systems in the pandemic by examining the YouTube platform. YouTube has been one of the more proactive platforms in attempting to stem the tide of misinformation, and its use of automated systems have deleted many videos with supposedly misinforming content. Using a content analysis and close reading of videos from channels sampled throughout 2020, this paper will identify approaches purveyors of misinformation have taken to exploit these automated solutions and theorize the conceptual limitations of the automated, content-based approach YouTube and other social media companies are taking in addressing the spread of misinformation in this pandemic.

The Technological Oculus of our Learning: Examining the Impact of AI and Big Data on Meaningful Learning Contexts *Nayah Boucaud, Indiana University*

The tumultuous ramifications of the COVID-19 pandemic have sparked millions of educators and students worldwide to transition permanently to digital learning environments and spaces. As a result, there has been an incline towards the implementation and use of digitized learning management systems (LMS) for supporting and supplementing disciplinary learning practices and spaces in digital platforms. These systems, such as Canvas (Instructure), Schoology (PowerSchool), and Google Classroom (Google Education); have become increasingly situative to the educator’s praxis (e.g., teaching, scaffolding) and the student’s learning and development, across myriad essentialized learning contexts. These LMSs increasingly utilize AI-oriented systems and data infrastructure to detect, track, and maintain certain metrics of students’ learning, engagement, collaboration, and assessment in real-time settings. Though some research has been conducted on the usefulness and efficiency of AI-based systems in learning contexts (Tsang, 2019; Mariachi, 2020), little research has explored whether the predictors of these computational structures are qualified to establish social, technological, or philosophical notions towards students’ cognitive and disciplinary abilities, processes, and experiences within meaningful learning contexts. As such, this paper will navigate social, cultural, and phenomenological ideologies uniform to the sociophilosophy of AI to further

examine the impact of AI-based tools on teachers' and students' engagement across different learning disciplines. This work highlights how digitized environments and embedded computational structures have the potential to indelibly transform teachers' and students' participation in the disciplinary learning practices and spaces most meaningful to their everyday learning. Works Referenced: Marachi, R., & Quill, L. (2020). The case of Canvas: Longitudinal datafication through learning management systems. *Teaching in Higher Education*, 25(4), 418-434. Tsang, W. (2019). A case study exploring high school teachers' perceptions of usefulness and ease of use of canvas learning management system (Doctoral dissertation, Northcentral University).

Bans, Censorship, and the Alt-Right: A Reddit Case Study
Vivian Ferrillo, Indiana University

Reddit and other social media companies have faced increasing criticism for inadvertently providing a platform for far-right groups and misinformation. The problem of extremist groups forming on otherwise harmless social media platforms and normalizing extreme ideologies is unlikely to go away soon. However, blindly encouraging social media companies to perform mass censorship runs a number of risks, including worsening the problem. This project interrogates the censorship tactic Reddit employed to oust alt-right members from its platform in 2017: outright banning of the r/altright subreddit. Advocates of this tactic believe that banning offending communities is the only way to remove a noxious presence and protect other users from doxing or harassment. However, theories of online censorship observe that successful censorship of information or ideas is nearly impossible as users can reroute information networks around the obstruction. To test the effectiveness of the subreddit banning tactic, this project capitalizes on a natural experiment formed when Reddit banned the controversial r/altright in February 2017. I test if r/altright members were willing to reroute to a similar subreddit following the ban, and whether they displayed chilled or backlash after doing so. I find that thousands of users did reroute to r/The_Donald, and that the most active users were the most likely to take the leap. I also find that rerouted users displayed backlash behaviors by posting even more often after their banning experience. This suggests that censorship tactics like banning may not be the most effective tools against online extremism.

"From ethics to law and fundamental rights. What can we learn from the EU's efforts to govern AI? Maya Mitre, Copenhagen Business School

The European Commission has recently announced a bold proposal for regulating Artificial Intelligence through a risk-based approach. AI is not the first controversial technology that the European Union sets out to regulate. However, it might be one of the broadest and most pervasive. In this paper, I apply the comparative method as a means to shed light into the particular challenges (legal, political and moral) involved in the governance of AI. More specifically, I compare the European Union's effort to govern two apparently different, though similarly controversial, technologies, namely, AI and gene editing. Differently from comparatists who aim at understanding why a given technology leads to different regulatory outcomes across countries (Ramjoue 2008) or "political cultures" (Jasanoff 2007), I keep the "jurisdiction" variable constant. My hope is both to (a) discern the particular challenges, if any, involved in AI governance, and (b) to analyze the degree to which a precautionary approach is applied to both fields. I depart from the hypothesis that the proposal for regulating AI as such, instead of its products, as in the case of gene editing, points at the existence of particularities in this technology, which in turn justify a stricter regulatory framework.

Session Organizer:

Katreen Boustani, Indiana University - Bloomington

Chairs:

Hamid Ekbia

Katreen Boustani, Indiana University - Bloomington

Discussant:

Hamid Ekbia

407. The Material-Semiotics of Global Health Infrastructures II: Valuations and Expansions

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

What can be made of built and provisional global health infrastructures? How do we begin to depict and analyse the complex workings and material heterogeneity of sprawling networks of people, evidentiary systems, communication channels, and the mundane and seemingly 'micro'-interacting components and artefacts that make-up, and are made up by, global health work? This panel thinks with and through the many questions raised by the persistence of global health infrastructures, bringing together case studies that centre their coexistence, adaptability, and fragility to challenge the "modern infrastructure ideal" (Furlong 2014). We suggest that the dispersed relations, affects, and transactions that characterize these sociotechnical systems enact and assign meaning to (racial, sexual, gender) differences that congeal infrastructures. In this, we move beyond viewing difference (e.g., non-heterosexuality or blackness) as merely fraught, socially constructed variable that facilitates interventions into health or behaviour. Instead, we consider how forms of difference are conjured, orchestrated, and sedimented within global health infrastructures. Questions pertinent to our discussions include: How are colonial, racialized, gendered, and other tropes, stereotypes, and assumptions reshuffled and recycled in submerged, non-explicit ways in present-day global health worlds? How do global health infrastructures work—not only through multiple layerings of mutually reinforcing networks—but also, more dissonantly, through less-visible repurposings and co-optations that meet unacknowledged exigencies contradictory to the aims of their original architecture? How do we understand and analyze productions and valuations of deprivation and difference—the vital substrates on which global health infrastructures materialize, animate, flourish, and come undone?

Participants:

Regulating difference: technologies of transparency in the pharmaceutical South
Ramah McKay, University of Pennsylvania

Research on pharmaceuticals has reflected on commodity flows within and across the Global South. In these accounts, "the South" appears at once as anti-capitalist project and as emerging market, a site of resistance to the hegemony of the North and of intense political and economic experimentation. In this paper, I draw from fieldwork with drug manufacturers, importers, and distributors in Maputo, Mozambique and Mumbai India to ask how technologies and infrastructures of pharmaceutical regulation both rely on and produce notions of racialized difference as well as claims to political alterity. I examine the claims made regarding technologies of inspection and regulation, on the one hand, and notions of safety, risk, postcolonial identity, and essentialized notions of industrial origin, on the other. Through attention to the material practices and infrastructures through which pharmaceutical production is made transparent, I explore how the semiotics of racialized and political difference work to stabilize ambivalent histories of connection, distribution, and (partial) regulation.

Care in Fragments: The Afterlives of Mobile Health Infrastructure in Burkina Faso
Vincent Duclos, Université du Québec à Montréal

This paper discusses MOS@N, a mobile health (mHealth) intervention which, during three years, monitored maternal and child health in the district of Nouna, in rural Burkina Faso. The paper examines the labors, materials and incommensurable experiences involved in holding MOS@N together. It pays

special attention to the work of “godmothers,” hired community relays who operated mobile phones, kept track of pregnant women, accompanied them for appointment, and helped with deliveries. The paper attends to the fragile, makeshift connections but also the hard, time-consuming work out of which spaces of care were effectively crafted in MOS@N. Care, in MOS@N, materialized in fragments. MOS@N was also only made to work as a result of an entire repurposing of the original project architecture. But in spite of, or perhaps because of this, almost four years after the project ran out of funding, MOS@N keeps persisting. Even as it was formally shut down, and technology is slowly decaying, godmothers are still at work. On the one hand, this work is now carried mostly on a voluntary basis, which undermines some of the original purposes of MOS@N, and (re)produces gendered forms of social obligation. On the other hand, fragmentation may also give rise to, intensify, and pluralize the relations that hold and support lives. MOS@N’s fragments are not broken parts of a whole. Against the persistent charms of unity, they exist and endure in their own way. Ultimately, this paper explores how the story of MOS@N might help us challenge imaginations of global health futures.

Categories and Crisis: Definitions of Essential in the COVID-19 Pandemic *Joshua Morris Hurwitz, Stanford GSB*

Crises occur when risks become elevated and unmanaged, such that the organization’s continued existence comes into question, requiring swift, yet ambiguous action to resolve (Pearson and Clair 1998). To overcome crises, organizational decision-makers moot possible strategies. I propose here that crisis strategies have a common structure, containing crisis-specific actions overlaid upon a mapping of activities and functions that will be maintained, restricted, and curtailed. When enacted, such strategies serve to allocate rights, resources, and risks via these features. Second, I consider how crisis solution/strategies come to be devised, suggesting that they become Latourian heterogeneous networks of actors, ideas, and concepts, rife with both inconsistencies and interdependencies. A case study of the delineation of “essential businesses” during the COVID-19 pandemic is used to illustrate the process.

Human Gamete Banking: Translating Metaphors of the Bank in Speculative Biocapital *Stu Marvel, Dept of Women's, Gender, and Sexuality Studies, Emory University*

This paper will take up the conceptual category of the sperm/ova bank in order to think more closely about how metaphors of financialization and efficiency operate within the context of human fertility and reproduction (Hurlburt 2015). It will analyze the biomaterial archive of human gamete banks, and trace the ways in which the category of the “bank” moves across multiple forms of biocapitalist production – sperm bank, blood bank, gene bank, seed bank, etc. How, if at all, has queer/feminist/decolonial jurisprudence responded to the conceptual financialization of these technoscientific practices? Why has the bank become the dominant metaphor, and how has the translation of this metaphor across globally-situated ‘biobanks’ structured conceptual frameworks and contributed to affirming the violences embedded within colonial legal languages of property and contract? By taking up these questions of property and contract in relation to human biomaterials, this paper aims to better understand recent moves toward speculative value, such as predictive egg freezing (Van de Wiel 2020; see also Bahng 2017). It builds upon existing scholarship such as Kara Swanson’s *Banking on the Body* (2014), while contextualizing more recent moves from the bank as repository to a site of speculative reinvestment (Breithoff and Harrison 2020). What might we learn here about the coproduction of identity and technoscience at the intersection of law, medicine and capital? The paper will conclude by offering a feminist and reproductive justice framework, in moving toward an anti/decolonial reimagining of the languages of property and value within the context of human gamete preservation.

More-than-human infrastructures and antimicrobial resistance:

An ethicopolitical account *Jose A. Cañada, University of Exeter; Salla Sariola, University of Helsinki; Andrea Butcher, University of Helsinki*

The phenomenon of antimicrobial resistance (AMR) brings renewed opportunities to understand the connections between global health and locally situated social materialities. Like other global health areas, AMR is not alien to North-South dynamics of inequality and colonialism. However, AMR poses specificities worth exploring. Most prominently, its One Health framing has led WHO to cooperate with FAO and OIE, going beyond its traditional area of action. Accordingly, the heterogeneous networks that characterise global health infrastructure expand to include actors from animal and environmental health sectors, including nonhumans like animals, plants, or water bodies. From an STS perspective, this requires a more-than-human outlook that has not always been central in analyses of global health infrastructure (with important exceptions like zoonoses), providing insights that go beyond usual humanist perspectives. The multisectoral ambitions of AMR initiatives often encounter asymmetries in capacity between sectors, especially in the areas of surveillance, data production, and guideline enforcement support, key elements to compensate for the lack of data and understanding of AMR as an emerging phenomenon. This translates into a lack of scalable recommendations and the difficulty to implement plans locally to support relevant actors like policy makers, scientists, doctors, veterinarians, breeders, and patients. This presentation uses material gathered by following these actors in a precarious setting, that of West Africa, to present an ethicopolitical account of the local sociomaterial relationalities that are often at odds with global health frameworks that present data, individual responsibility and reduced antibiotic use as the only alternatives to the challenge of AMR.

“It Looks Like a Jail”: On Global Mental Health Infrastructures in a Tanzanian Psychiatric Ward *Bryan Dougan, UNC-Chapel Hill*

This paper examines idealized global mental health infrastructures in the context of a psychiatric ward in Dar es Salaam, Tanzania. Psychiatric wards, and hospitals more broadly, are microcosms of global health infrastructures and reflect broader ideological shifts in culture and medicine. Proponents of “post-asylum” and deinstitutionalized approaches to psychiatric care argued against aesthetics of confinement and overcrowding in the redesign of psychiatric wards. I examine both the jail-like appearance of the Tanzanian ward and Tanzanian psychiatrists’ past and present efforts to renovate the ward to reveal how the built ward itself contains colonial and carceral infrastructures despite efforts to move away from these kinds of treatment facilities. Drawing on ethnographic encounters and the design of the ward itself, I argue the Tanzanian ward illuminates how the infrastructures embedded in the built architecture of the ward operate in opposition to contemporary Global Mental Health ideals. Focusing on the Tanzanian ward thus reveals broader inequalities about how some mental health infrastructures get repurposed in global mental health and some do not.

Session Organizer:

Robert Lorway, University of Manitoba

Chair:

Robert Lorway, University of Manitoba

Discussant:

Claire Wendland, University of Wisconsin-Madison

408. (Re)materialising Cancer: Bodies, Cells and Environments - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Bioscientific approaches to identifying, classifying and diagnosing cancer have long enrolled practices that engage with the materiality of tumour tissues and cells, such as cytology and histology. In the contemporary era, scientific techniques detect and act upon cancer outwith tumour tissue itself. For example, pre-cells, inflammatory cells, immune system T cells and microbes are becoming understood to play a role in cancer. Molecular pathology has also allowed for exploration of the makeup of cancerous tissues as inscribed within genetic code, and can 'diagnose' predispositions to cancer. Such techniques, along with designations of cells as 'pre-cancerous', add a temporal dimension to the materiality of cancer. These approaches locate cancer within structures and organisms beyond the tangibility of tumour tissue, and demonstrate that various elements of bodies and their environments continuously interact to constitute the disease. Contemporary scientific work thus generates a picture of cancer as more than malignant, fleshy tumours, with the disease materialising in genes, healthy cells, and wider (bodily) environments. This refigures the material constitution of cancer, blurs clinical categorisations of tissues and cells as malignant or benign, and prompts us to think about cancer in ways that unsettle widespread 'fixed' sociocultural understandings of the disease. In this session we will discuss configurations of cancer that disrupt understandings of the disease as manifested in a malignant, fleshy, tumour. We ask 'what constitutes cancer?' and address the implications of these diverse configurations for scientific and clinical practice, embodied experiences, patient subjectivities, and sociocultural depictions of cancer.

Participants:

The Journey of T cells into CAR T cells: from the Body to the Bench and Back *Isabel Briz Hernandez, Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Based on 15 months of fieldwork on oncology trials for immunotherapy in China, in this paper, I explore how cancer and its treatment is redefined through T-cells and CAR T-cells. In recent years, immunotherapy, especially Chimeric Antigen Receptor (CAR) T-cell therapy has come to be considered a breakthrough in cancer and a promising new pillar for its treatment. This new therapy is a personalised 'living drug' that aims to enhance the potential of the immune system to cure. T-cells are extracted from the patients' body, harvested, genetically edited and injected back into the patient. As the name of the therapy describes, a chimera, that consists in a T-cell surface and a synthetic T-cell receptor, is created to target precisely the specific antigen of each patient's cancer cells. In the postgenomic era, T-cells emerge as a valuable asset for scientific and medical experimentation. However, it's a scarce asset, white cell levels tend to be low in immunocompromised patients. Moreover, previous treatments have frequently deteriorated significantly the veins, making the apheresis, the medical procedure to collect T-cells, a painful experience for patients and a tedious endeavour for nurses and doctors. Understanding that T-cells and CAR T cells "are not 'discovered', they are made and remade in relation to shifting contexts" (Hardon and Sanabria 2017:117), in this paper, I illustrate the journey of T-cells into CAR T-cells pointing to how on each interaction with nurses, doctors, couriers, lab technicians, scientists and patients themselves they get redefined according to different values, expectations and experiences.

Enrolling The Body As Active Agent In Disease Treatment: Tracing Immune System And Cancer Relations *Julia Swallow, University of Edinburgh*

Immunotherapy is an emerging biotechnology in the treatment of advanced cancer and has been heralded as the 'fifth pillar' of cancer therapy after surgery, radiotherapy, chemotherapy and genomic medicine. Two specific types have emerged in clinical practice and/or are being tested as part of clinical trials in the UK: checkpoint inhibitors and chimeric antigen receptor T-cell (CAR T) therapy. These therapies involve harnessing or reprogramming patients' own immune system T cells to 'attack' cancer, potentially leading to long-term survival and cure. Militaristic metaphors pervade immunity discourse concerning

immunotherapy whilst the immune system is also framed as agile and adaptable, (re)figuring distinctions of self/other, internal/external as the patient's own body becomes active agent in treatment, bolstering the personalisation agenda in cancer. Drawing on documentary analysis and interview data, this paper explores the social, cultural and experiential significance of the mobilisation of the patient's own immune system as 'weapon', or 'saviour' in the long-term treatment for their cancer. In so doing, addressing the entanglements between discursive representations of the relationship between the immune system and cancer and the material realities of immune system/cancer relations, including the impact of these therapies on embodied experiences of cancer, practices of cancer and disease ontologies.

Precision immuno-oncology and patient-experience measurements: a perspective within a co-design research *Nils Graber, STS Lab, University of Lausanne*

Precision immuno-oncology is relying on both immunotherapies and infrastructures of genomics. It is an emerging field requiring the development of new platforms to select therapies according to actionable pathways, but also by considering new biological entities such as the tumor micro-environment, neoantigens, or other immune-related biomarkers. Furthermore, such oncological domain is characterized by the manufacturing of patient-tailored treatments relying on autologous cells, such as adoptive cell therapies (using TILs, CAR-T...) or therapeutic vaccination. Based on intensive production of data, precision immuno-oncology is also integrated in clinical practices through personalized experimental care. These latter are increasingly including data stemming from the patients, such as patient reported-outcomes measures (PROMS) to identify unknown immune-related adverse reactions, which are more generally part of the promissory project of enhancing participation within biomedicine. In this paper, we explore the understanding of cancer underpinning a program of 'co-design' aiming at grasping the experience of patients receiving adoptive cell therapy (ACT) in the context of phase I clinical trials. Drawing on early participant observation work related to the study protocol's conception, we will discuss how the understanding of cancer - in relation to both the epistemic specificity of the immune system and the organization of autologous cell treatments - is shaping the way of envisioning patienthood in such experimental settings. We shall also analyze the understanding of patients' experiences in relation to both the on-going process of datafication and the making of new biomedical platforms.

Individual Genome Meets Cancer Genome: Personalising Cancer Research and Treatment *Maria Temmes, Tampere University*

A systems approach to cancer research has gained ground in recent years, establishing new research projects aiming to bring molecular level research closer to clinics to form new personalised treatment options. This presentation examines how the idea of personalisation is enacted in systems medicine research practices. Based on my fieldwork at the Institute for Molecular Medicine Finland, I will show how individualised systems medicine in cancer research balances between immediate clinical applicability and examination of disease mechanisms. Following Bruno Latour's suggestion that social scientists should always first let the actors themselves to define what they do, I will argue that rather than seeing systems medicine as a well-defined approach in medical research a more fruitful way to discuss the changes brought by systems approaches is to consider how the relevance of medical research is increasingly tied into the question of contextual interactions in disease models. While systems medicine has its foundation in systems biology, the need to form clinically relevant research also forms new questions about the reliability of different kinds of models when thinking of the possibilities to represent the complex interactions in human bodies.

Session Organizers:

Emily Ross, The University of Sheffield
Julia Swallow, University of Edinburgh

Chair:

Lisa Ashmore, Lancaster University, UK

Discussant:

Lisa Lindén, Department of Sociology and Work Science,
University of Gothenburg

409. Studying Humans and Technology in Medical Contexts in Japan

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Over the past decades, there has been an increase in technological innovation in hospitals, influencing medical practices and regulatory requirements alike. What is more, there can be observed a thrust of technological progress at high pace in the field of biomedical engineering and medical informatics at present, which contributes additionally to new configurations of technological landscapes in hospitals in Japan. The meaning of socio-technical settings in the medical field changes not only with their professional, disciplinary or organisational context, but also with the specific locale. This panel therefore elucidates how the relationship between humans and technology can be specified in medical contexts when the sociocultural dimension of a particular locale is included. More precisely, the panel explores the ways in which socio-technical settings in medical contexts find varying articulations in a specific locale like Japan. Specifically, the panel briefly introduces a theoretical approach by specifying the Japanese locale (*genba*) as an example when examining socio-technical settings in medical contexts. Thereafter, three papers will reflect on emerging high-technology as well as the arising requirements and controversies regarding aspects such as patient security, end-of-life decisions and evaluation of novel devices. The papers will situate their case studies of technological landscapes in hospitals in their given semantic, pragmatic, organisational and/or historical context, thereby enriching academic discussions on socio-technical settings in medical contexts amongst affiliated disciplines. The panel is part of an ongoing book project (by Susanne Brucksch and Kaori Sasaki).

Participants:

The Formulation of Japanese Standardised Brain-Death Diagnostic Procedure *Kaori Sasaki*, *Sapporo Medical University*

This presentation explores the ways in which the Japanese brain-death diagnostic procedure was formulated in the 1980s-1990s. From 1968 to the early 1980s, countries such as the UK, USA, and Taiwan had seen the definition of end of life change from cardio-respiratory failure to irreversible deep coma—later termed brain-death; meanwhile the medical authorities of those countries established standardised brain-death diagnostic procedures. These changes derived from the emergence of the clinical application of an automatic artificial ventilator, and of cardiac transplantation. The transplantation procedure requires a surgeon to extract a pumping heart from a donor; the ventilator device allows the cardio-respiratory function of an irreversible deep coma patient to continue despite a total failure in brain function. Therefore, a beating heart could be taken from a brain-dead donor's body for transplantation. In Japan, the medical community attempted to follow these precedents but there arose a controversy as to which medical technology should be applied: electroencephalogram (EEG), auditory brainstem response (ABR), and/or cerebral angiography. More precisely, the Japanese brain-death diagnostic procedure was shaped alongside intensive reflection over not only which medical technology would be more reliable and feasible to confirm brain-death accurately, but also which cultural position should be taken; that is, whether Japan should follow British, US or Swedish practice, or adopt an alternative approach. Examination of this controversy illuminates how socio-culturally constructed images were inscribed in the usage of each of the medical technologies

relevant to the brain-death diagnostic procedure.

Patients' Subjective Evaluation: The Cyborg-type Robot HAL and the Treatment of Functional Regeneration in Patients with Rare Incurable Neuromuscular Diseases *Nakajima Takashi*, *Niigata National Hospital, Japan*

The WHO definition of health as complete well-being is widely accepted. However, this definition has been criticised as being less feasible for incurable diseases and for the increase in chronic illnesses in aging societies such as Japan. Therefore, this paper refers to the alternative concept of health suggested by Huber et al. (2011) as the "ability to adapt and self-manage in the face of social, physical, and emotional challenges". Accordingly, medical treatment could be interpreted as support for patients to adapt to certain disabilities instead of efforts towards normalization. One medical treatment based on the alternative concept is the medical treatment with a cyborg-type robot Hybrid Assistive Limb (HAL). HAL was developed by Yoshiyuki Sankai as a device for motor learning. He is a scientist who has innovatively conceptualised *Cybernetics*, a term that is coined from cybernetics, mechatronics, and informatics. Subsequently, a multi-institutional research group centred at Niigata National Hospital in Kashiwazaki City performed a randomised clinical trial (NCY-3001) for gait treatment with HAL in patients with incurable neuromuscular diseases. During the clinical trial and in this paper, our research team argues that the patients' subjective evaluations that are patient-reported outcomes (PRO) should be strengthened as evidence of adaptation and improvement of symptoms.

Incident reporting systems to improve patient safety in Japanese hospitals *NAONORI KODATE*, *University College Dublin*

Safety has been given serious attention in many high-risk domains in Japan and elsewhere. Healthcare has been relatively slow in responding to the development of safety science. However, attempts have been made to reform the regulation of risks to patients since the 1990s in many countries, and Japan is no exception. Nationally, the Japan Council for Quality Health Care manages the web-based reporting system and collects data about serious adverse events and incidents on a voluntary basis. This paper compares how hospitals in Japan and England use their respective reporting systems as a source of learning, and highlights the importance of cultural and institutional contexts when examining sociotechnical settings in healthcare. While this study was modelled upon that previously carried out in England, the scope of this paper is broader, and targeted at country-level comparison. Moreover, semi-structured interviews were conducted with patient-safety managers in three different types of hospitals in Japan and experts in four European countries. Our findings from the various frameworks and the patient safety managers' perceptions suggest that web-based reporting became an important tool but human-to-human interactions and national policy contexts remain critical for understanding incident reporting and patient safety.

Session Organizer:

Susanne Brucksch, DIJ Tokyo

410. The Code of Beauty: How Aesthetics Shape and Structure Technosciences

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Robert Oppenheimer famously explained the eagerness with which physicists took up the development of the atomic bomb by describing the lure of projects that are "technically sweet." As his aphorism shows, the formal work of scientific and technical communities is embedded with affective and aesthetic cultures that sanction and shape technical work. Competing and shifting aesthetic frameworks mark out the multiple communities of practice that make up technical fields and their audiences and can celebrate, erase, or justify different elements of technoscientific practice. This makes for a particularly complex landscape in cases of

interdisciplinary work where different aesthetic systems rub up against each other. This panel will explore the role of aesthetic discourse in technical communities and how an orientation towards different aesthetic judgments shapes the evaluation of both problems and solutions. By looking across multiple empirical domains, we will attempt to document the varieties of aesthetic reasoning and discourse that characterize different spheres of technoscientific practice and explore opportunities for a more coherent account of aesthetics as an aspect of everyday work in technical domains.

Participants:

The Good, the Bad, and the Ugly Code: The Role of Aesthetics in Programming Practices *Marina Fedorova, University of California - Irvine; Paul Dourish, University Of California Irvine; Melissa Mazmanian, University of California, Irvine*

The field of technosciences has been traditionally seen as the major domain where rationality lives. Computer science is not an exception to this rule. Practices of writing code have been trapped in the tradition of positivistic thinking and are often discursively rid of any messiness associated with both human or non-human forces. We argue that what often subtly evades our research attention is aesthetics. We are going to discuss how developers use the language of aesthetics to describe their practices. In our study, we found that considerations of beauty and aesthetics are not only incidental to programming practice, but often shape the ways in which engineers communicate about code. Aesthetic language is used to organize activities and establish best practices in engineering. In the case of programming, the focus on beauty and ugliness of code allows us to reveal how aesthetic judgments about code can structure technoscientific work.

Environmental Sensors and Aesthetic Publics Along the Chattahoochee River *Yanni Alexander Loukissas, Georgia Institute of Technology*

In recent years, social studies of environmental sensors have exposed their entanglements within more-than-human assemblages, as part of smart cities, wilderness monitoring, or climate modeling (Gabrys 2019). Such studies provocatively decenter our own aesthetic experiences of sensing. They reveal how sensing can be enacted through digital cycles of stimulus and response that occur entirely outside of our own bodies (Helmreich 2019). However, externalized sensing technologies are no less important to our collective perceptions of the environment. In this talk, I reflect on how environmental sensors shape and are shaped by the formation of "aesthetic publics" (Michael 2018). These groups, united by common matters of concern, seek to frame nature in terms of what is beautiful and desirable, and what is not. Moreover, I explore how participatory art and design projects can use environmental sensors, and the data they generate, to shift aesthetic publics or mobilize new ones (Le Dantec and DiSalvo 2013). Such creative uses can effectively open up these technologies (Stirling 2008) to alternative aesthetic conceptions of nature. My case study is a water monitoring project along the Chattahoochee, a river in the Southeastern United States that runs from North Georgia to the border of Florida, and is the most widely used water resource in the state.

The Aesthetics of "Away" in Technology Sustainability *Dawn Nafus, Intel*

No one is surprised about the environmental costs of SUVs or flying, yet there seems to be a perpetual surprise when data about the environmental costs of information and communication technologies (ICTs) becomes apparent. This talk will explore the social and material reasons why the environmental costs of ICTs are regularly unseen. It will seek to get beyond simple explanations like the popular faith in "the digital" as somehow defying materiality, or greenwashing practices. While both are very real, they cannot fully explain the glimmers of recognition that do exist. Instead, I will explore the apparent relationship between the aesthetics of different components of interdependent

systems—data centers versus connectivity networks, large language models versus less spectacular ones—and the choices being made about the kinds of energy consumption that are characterized and measured, and the consumption that floats into the ether as a kind of "away." By examining the visual imaginaries associated with these objects, we get a glimpse into the social life of seeing and unseeing environmental harm.

Aesthetics as a Technical Controversy for Artificial Intelligence *Warren Sack, University of California, Santa Cruz*

At the very beginning of artificial intelligence (AI), coding commonsense was seen as an essential, technical problem. In an essay published in 1958, John McCarthy — co-founder of the field and the convener of the 1956 summer workshop at Dartmouth that started it all — envisioned an "advice taker" system that could be programmed in everyday language by conversing with a human. The stumbling block foreseen was that the system would only be able to absorb those statements for which it had background knowledge or "commonsense" adequate to fill in the details or the context of the advice given: what goes up must come down — except if you are an astronaut in space. In 1998, when I wrote the entry for "artificial intelligence" in the Oxford Encyclopedia of Aesthetics, I argued that Kantian aesthetics — that takes commonsense as a governing concern for aesthetic judgment — was a framework one could employ to understand decades of work in AI on commonsense reasoning. However, between then and now, decades of new work in machine learning hint that commonsense might be squeezed out of vast repositories of big data thus making unnecessary special techniques of programming and formalization or one-on-one dialogical interaction (like McCarthy's advice taker). And, yet, those who have been working on the problem for decades do not necessarily agree that machine learning is a solution. For example, Gary Marcus and Ernest Davis at NYU have recently written, "Deep learning, which lacks a direct way of incorporating abstract knowledge (like "People want to recover things they've lost") has largely ignored the problem [of commonsense]." Interestingly, to explain the current state of AI and commonsense Marcus and Davis cite Kant's Critique of Pure Reason and not his Critique of Judgment (on aesthetics) that I cite in my 1998 article. This paper will unfold several empirical questions: What is commonsense and for whom, in the AI community, is it (still) a central problem? And, is the prospect of coding commonsense an issue of aesthetics as I argue and as recent books, like Winnie Soon and Geoff Cox's 2021 *Aesthetic Programming: A Handbook of Software Studies* would seem to imply?

Session Organizers:

Marina Fedorova, University of California - Irvine
Paul Dourish, University Of California Irvine
Melissa Mazmanian, University of California, Irvine

Discussant:

Paul Dourish, University Of California Irvine

411. The Spectacular: Science, Technology, and Wondrous Relations

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Recently, STS practitioners have turned their attention to "the speculative" (Benjamin 2016, Haraway 2016, Rees and Morus 2019). Meanwhile, questions around its homonymological cousin, "the spectacular," have lain dormant. This panel explores the relationships between these phenomena and aligned practices of speculating and producing spectacles. Drawing inspiration from Daston and Park's (1998) classic work on wonder as a mode of affective inquiry - and challenging their conclusion that wonder is not a constitutive dimension of late modern science - we focus on larger than life tales told about and with technoscience, considering how wonder expands the relations to which STS ought attend. This exploration of the spectacular unfolds across time and space, ranging from the transnational

travels of woolly mammoth specimens in the 19th century to the late 20th century technoscientific fabrications of Michael Crichton to contemporary science fiction film production in South Africa and to the world-building practices of Hollywood's virtual reality innovators. In each case, relations are forged between heterogeneous communities joined together to realize and manifest the spectacular. What groups of people or what kinds of expertise are drawn into this technoscientific work that are traditionally not seen as mattering? To what overlooked locations of labor and expertise does this draw our attention? Our papers employ the concept of the spectacular not to reify technoscience's position in society, but rather to draw upon its charisma in order to redirect the analytic gaze to the scaffolding upon which such displays are built.

Participants:

'Mad Max Territory': Global Hollywood and the Impractical Effects of Climate Crisis in South Africa *Jessica Dickson, Harvard University*

: In 2018, the Western Cape province of South Africa faced an unprecedented drought. In an urgent effort to persuade residents to reduce water usage, Cape Town city officials implemented a usage-contingent countdown to what became known as "Day Zero": the day the taps run dry. A title befitting a blockbuster, Day Zero was effective in capturing the attention of more than just Capetonians. As Time Magazine published drone images of suburbanites lining up for water, describing the city as "Mad Max Territory," Cape Town's economy saw a dramatic drop in international investment. Despite its reference to the 2015 multiple-Oscar winner, the Time article made no mention that significant production on Mad Max: Fury Road had in fact taken place in the Western Cape, and with Cape Town-based crew servicing shoots in Namibia. What Cape Town's water crisis made clear was that while the appearances of apocalyptic conditions proved valuable to Hollywood genre trends, actual climatological fallout was not conducive to the strict environmental control required for big-budget film production. This paper examines how stakeholders in Cape Town's film-service industry sought to simultaneously assuage and capitalize on the spectacle of Day Zero, while also navigating the precarity of water scarcity and dependence on foreign investment.

Domesticating the Spectacular: Worldbuilding, Virtual Reality, and Civic Engagement *Lisa Messeri, Yale University*

Worldbuilding is an approach developed by speculative fiction authors and Hollywood creatives for envisioning detailed worlds that, when imaginatively set in motion, generate stories to be told. While conducting ethnographic fieldwork in Los Angeles, I encountered worldbuilding as a method used both in developing virtual reality experiences and imagining civic futures. This paper traces how worldbuilding became a method that can be deployed to produce a VR spectacle and also to rally citizen and government stakeholders around tackling urban problems. In the first context, worldbuilding pushes the bounds of the technoscience imagination. In the second context, worldbuilding pushes the bounds of the societal imagination. This paper explores how Hollywood players imagine themselves as simultaneously creating fantastical storyworlds for technological consumption and doing "on the ground work" of forging good relations to build better communities.

Building Block(busters) of Life: Jurassic Park and The Spectacular Manifestations of STS *Joanna Radin, Yale School of Medicine*

: A few years after delivering the keynote at the opening of the MIT Media Lab in 1985, author, producer and director, Michael Crichton took up a fellowship at the prestigious Knight Science Writing program at MIT where he taught a class in "non-fiction writing." Cambridge had become a kind of East Coast Silicon Valley, flush with speculative capital for biotech and informatics. MIT, home also to an influential Science and Technology Studies program, left its mark on his writing, evident in invocations of the scholarship of feminist historians of science and technology,

Carolyn Merchant and Ruth Schwartz Cowan in his biggest hit, Jurassic Park, published in 1990. This talk focuses on Jurassic Park, both the novel and the 1993 movie, directed by Steven Spielberg, to demonstrate how feminist and colonial critiques of science were reproduced—and neutered—in the context of the blockbuster novel, a new Hollywood studio system, in subsequent genomic scientific initiatives and STS itself. Jurassic Park, in its surrealistic and spectacular depictions of dinosaurs living alongside humans, breathed life into very real systems of capitalism and biotech, even as it reshaped the terms of political as well as intellectual debate over meanings of life, science, and its social study.

Pleistocene Spectacular: Frozen Mammoths and Fantastic Displays in 19th- and 20th-century Natural History *Rebecca JH Woods, Columbia University*

Frozen mammoths are among the most spectacular of natural history specimens. Their wondrous preservation across tens of thousands of years in the permafrost of Siberia, and the visceral link between deep past and present that their frozen bodies offer, hold special appeal to scientific and lay audiences alike. But the cultural appeal of frozen mammoths is sometimes at odds with the sensory reality of their remains. While drawings, depictions, prints, and models based on frozen mammoths have long held wide appeal for museum goers and reading publics, the fragments of hair, skin, tissue, and blood found behind the scenes in museum collections are considerably less charismatic. Ragged, sometimes smelly remains are discordant with the awe-inspiring time-transgressing reputation of frozen mammoths. Using examples from the nineteenth and twentieth centuries, this paper explores the relationship between the spectacular frozen mammoth and its unimpressive biomaterial traces, asking what wondrous transformations and relations go into the making of the Pleistocene spectacular?

Session Organizer:

Lisa Messeri, Yale University

Chair:

Edward Jones-Imhotep, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Edward Jones-Imhotep, University of Toronto

412. Diverse, inclusive and caring engineering relations I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

This panel invites papers that studies efforts to make engineering and engineering education more inclusive, diverse and caring. Engineers engage in design, development, testing, modifying, installing, inspecting, monitoring and maintaining a wide variety of infrastructures, systems and products. They make recommendations, evaluate, supervise, consult and some of them teach future engineers in colleges and universities. Engineers potentially play a pivotal role in designing for a more diverse, inclusive and caring society in the future. We call for papers that analyze attempts to make engineering more diverse and/or caring. This could be efforts to redefine engineering practices or engineering education. Broadly speaking, this include studies of initiatives to transform engineering practices, organizations and cultures to make them more caring, ethical, diverse and inclusive and thus helping to develop a more sustainable society that protect people, cultures, communities and environments. It also invites papers about how to make engineering more welcome and inclusive for groups and minorities. It also welcomes paper discussing the need to change the understanding of engineering and what engineers are for, what changes that are called for, and what this may mean for engineering identities. Further, we welcome critical reflections on research practices, methodologies, language and perceptions in engineering studies, including the performativity of engineering studies and reflections on what represent good relations for engineering as well as reflections on how the field may configure engineers and engineering work and education.

Participants:

Caring for Engineering Students through STS Knowledge and

Action Annie Y Patrick, Virginia Tech

Many engineering education researchers explore methods to broaden engineering students' attitudes to include social responsibility. Some suggest studying the significance of empathy within engineering. Others suggest delving further into engineering ethics. However, it is not enough for engineering students (and engineers) to be taught an awareness of the social impact of their work, but there must be a willingness to actively respond and care about the impact of their work upon society. Creating engineers that care about diversity, inclusion, and social equity begins with creating a caring environment for current and prospective engineer students. In this talk, I address this challenge by integrating the "matters of concern" and the "matters of care" within the engineering education culture. I draw from these two concepts to create an environment that is more conducive to inclusion and diversity and to foster engineers that think beyond the engineering process and consider the various people and communities that will be impacted by their work. I have utilized these two theories to develop three projects of engagement within an electrical and computer engineering (ECE) department to create a more inclusive sense of departmental belonging; to bring visibility to the invisible work of academic advising; and to create opportunities for career exploration. For this talk, I will focus on how I utilized podcasting to create inclusion in the ECE department by recognizing and sharing the voices of the engineering students that have experienced and overcome the challenges of being female, underrepresented, underserved, and unseen.

Good Intentions Are Not Enough: Student-led Interventions To Reconfigure Relationships Between Engineering, "Caring" & Development *Michael Solomon Reyna, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo; Gabriel Medina-Kim, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute; Krystal Cardenas, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo; Luka Uchiyama, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo; Jane L Lehr, California Polytechnic State University*

Student-led engineering development projects are examples of attempts to do good. However, the dominant model for development projects is largely based in neoliberal and neocolonial practices. Many student-led development projects - a common method of global competency education for engineers - focus more on what students can learn from their participation in these projects than on benefits to community partners (Lucena, Schneider, Leydens, 2010). While these projects are often labeled as successful, the reality is that these projects typically fail for students and communities (Nieusma & Riley, 2010). While this issue is now well known in STS, less attention has been directed to the self-critical and interventionist work of students engaged in development projects who seek to make visible and disrupt these structures of oppressions. This paper draws from semi-structured interviews with recent alumni of a student-led chapter of a U.S.-based non-profit that seeks to build "a better world through engineering projects that empower communities to meet their basic human needs and equip leaders to solve the world's most pressing challenges." The interviewees - during their participation as undergraduate students - had identified ways in which the good intentions of U.S.-based students do not result in good impacts and how dominant practices (including methods of the U.S.-based non-profit) perpetuate oppression. All interviewees also described efforts, successful and unsuccessful, to intervene structurally to create better relations with non-U.S. community partners. What can we learn from these students as we reconfigure engineering to create a more caring and equitable world?

Contextualization as Caring? The Roles of STS in Engineering Education *Kari Zacharias; Marie Stettler Kleine, Colorado School Of Mines; Desen Sevi Ozkan, Tufts University*

This paper characterizes and reflects on approaches to contextualization in engineering education, asking whether contextualizing engineering is sufficient to make change, and analyzing the roles of STS in engineering curriculum and pedagogy. As STS scholars and engineering educators, our attempts to make engineering more inclusive, diverse, and caring often cite the decontextualized nature of traditional engineering education (Buch & Bucciarelli, 2015; Leydens et al., 2018). By situating engineering with respect to its sociopolitical contexts, we argue that we can teach our students to understand engineering - accurately - as sociotechnical, to define and solve engineering problems effectively, and to address longstanding injustices. The paper first describes different STS-influenced modes of contextualization, including sociotechnical thinking approaches that emphasize complexity, problem definition, and value-ladenness, but generally refrain from making specific arguments about how engineering ought to be practiced; social justice-centered approaches that take a stronger normative stance; and recent work that argues for the integration of ethics of care in engineering education. We then reflect on the roles of STS in engineering education through our own experiences as educators. Contextualization alone is often insufficient to shift engineers' existing perceptions of their field as apolitical, meritocratic, and distinct from society (Cech, 2014). At the same time, for multiple reasons, we are wary of being overly prescriptive. We recognize in our own classroom experiences a tension between institutional realities, desire to affect change, and discomfort with normativity that reflects the range of roles that STS fulfills in engineering education.

Relationship-building and Role Perception in Engineering: A Critical Reflection *Ellen Lynch*

As local, national and global challenges increase in complexity, engineers are required to engage with an increasing number of diverse professionals. Successful collaboration across professions, sectors and cultures requires a high level of emotional intelligence, empathy, care and humility. These traits are beginning to be explored within engineering practice through understanding perceptions and perceived importance. However, literature and graduate accreditation frameworks emphasize the importance of 'communication' and 'professional' skills, rather than relationship-building and associated traits such as engagement skills, open-mindedness, empathy, humility and curiosity. This paper will argue that how these traits and habits of mind demonstrated within engineering practice can be viewed through collaborative and working relationships. And secondly, that relationship-building is an essential skill of an engineering professional, but is not explicitly or sufficiently emphasized in curriculum or accreditation frameworks. These conclusions follow research investigating how engineers build and maintain professional relationships, viewed through the lens of humility. This paper will be based on initial findings from 21 qualitative research interviews with mid-career engineering professionals in Australia from across sectors and disciplines. This work contributes to STS by highlighting the importance of authentic relationship building in engineering, and how it may be framed as a vital skill and mindset in other professions. It is hoped through framing dimensions of relationship building in this way, the engineering profession may become more empathic, aware, caring and humble, leading to more positive interactions and outcomes.

UAVs for Defense: Reflecting on Responsible Design Decisions *Robin Ann Downey, Bilkent University*

As part of the required Science, Technology and Society class at Bilkent University, engineering students investigate responsible innovation practices and conduct interviews with local innovators for their term project. Students often choose to interview engineers from companies that are working on Unmanned Aerial Vehicles (UAVs) for the defense sector. In the development of military UAVs, innovators clearly take into account instrumental

values, including efficiency and security. However, as part of their responsible innovation inquiries, students also examine qualitative values, including civilian risk, privacy, environmental aspects, and user considerations in design decisions. Emerging military technologies can significantly change existing socio-technical practices, presenting key decision makers with new challenges, as has been explored in the literature on “responsibility practices” (M. Noorman, 2014). The “responsibility practices” concept can help students effectively consider the role of users in the development of military technologies. The term project offers students an opportunity to move across academic boundaries, consult innovators and explore innovation practices in applied contexts. Engineering students can develop a fresh perspective on innovation possibilities, which may have implications for “engineering formation” (G.L. Downey, 2009). Students may uncover incremental adjustments made by innovators and imagine potential solutions for qualitative values. This presentation will use Responsible Innovation literature, including van de Poel’s work on values and design as the main theoretical lens. I will also draw on interviews with engineering students that have engaged with innovators who are developing UAVs for military purposes.

Session Organizers:

Vivian Anette Lagesen, NTNU

Atsushi Akeru, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Jessica Mary Smith, Colorado School of Mines

Cyrus Mody, Maastricht University

Chair:

Atsushi Akeru, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

413. Sense ecologies: new technologies and strategies of environmental surveillance - II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Drones and mounted cameras monitoring wildfire ignitions. Satellites detecting areas of deforestation and reforestation or the transport of agents through ocean currents. Weather stations tracking humidity and rainfall surrounding monocrops. Video cameras poised to capture evidence of rare or threatened species, while bodies and wearable medical devices register the presence and passage of industrial pollutants. Sensors and modes of sensing are part of infrastructures that monitor and mobilize environments, constituting atmospheres of data, knowledge production, and world-making (Gabrys 2019). These ‘sense ecologies’ are differentially charged with promise when imagined and enacted (Spackman and Burlingame 2018), sometimes with expectations that they might deliver a world without surprises (Masco 2014). In practice, the promise of recent and new environmental sensing technologies are highly ambivalent. Their proliferation has been crucial to projects that hold powerful state and non-state actors to account, while (often concurrently) being enlisted as vectors for state securitization, targeted discrimination, corporatization and neoliberal intrusion (Mansfield 2008). Whatever their use, new sensing technologies are powerful, often compromised (Liboiron 2017), and are increasingly widespread means for imagining, constituting and intervening in environments. This open panel seeks contributions that examine new techno-imaginaries of environmental surveillance, including (but not limited to) analyses of sense ecologies and their ‘good’ or ‘bad’ relations, sites and practices of sensing, the promises of sensing technologies, ecologies of attuned sensing, distributed sensing networks, and the privatisation of sense ecologies. References: Gabrys, Jennifer. 2019. Sensors and Sensing Practices: Reworking Experience across Entities, Environments, and Technologies. *Science, Technology & Human Values* 44 (5):723-736. Liboiron, Max. 2017. Compromised agency: The case of BabyLegs. *Engaging Science, Technology, and Society*, 3, 499-527. Mansfield, Becky, ed. 2008. *Privatization: property and the remaking of nature-society relations*. Oxford: Blackwell. Masco, Joseph. 2014. *The theater of operations: National security affect from the Cold War to the War on Terror*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press. Spackman, Christy, and Burlingame, Gary. A. 2018. Sensory politics: the tug-of-war between potability and palatability in municipal water production. *Social Studies of*

Science, 48(3): 350-371.

Participants:

Criminal Sounds: Hearing Illegality Through Acoustic Surveillance in Philippine Forests *Will Smith, Deakin University*

Technologies of visualization produce highly fragmented representations of tropical forests. Thick vegetation and cloud cover obscure the gaze of satellites, drones and camera traps. Following forest peoples around the world, ecological scientists are now engaged in a sensorial pivot to the auditory in the form of networked bioacoustic surveillance. Digital tools, distributed in forest landscapes, can algorithmically dissect forest cacophonies and monitor the movement and distribution of wildlife. Increasingly, however, the promised efficacy of acoustic surveillance has captured the interest of conservation organizations and state environmental managers as technology that can identify, in real time, illicit environmental behavior hidden by tree cover. This paper explores implementation of an acoustic surveillance system on Palawan Island in the Philippines, a country whose state foresters are enthusiastically integrating a range of new digital technologies to apprehend illegal loggers and wildlife traders. This system is composed of networked, solar powered mobile phones that can identify the “criminal sounds” emanating from chainsaws, firearms and motorcycles across vast distances. Palawan’s forests, however, are also the ancestral territory of thousands of indigenous people whose livelihoods often acoustically and legally slip into the realm of criminality. While emphasizing how these new technologies reproduce existing processes of indigenous marginalization by envisioning a forest sonically-free of all human activity, this paper also probes the distinct sensory politics that emerge from acoustic surveillance.

Technologies of the Body: The Social Production of Embodied Knowledge Among California’s Wildland Firefighters *Jordan C Thomas, University of California, Santa Barbara*

This paper examines the formation and use of embodied knowledge among California wildland firefighters. In 2020, firefighters worked along the edges of the largest blazes in California’s history. The lives of firefighters, communities, and ecologies often depend upon firefighters’ abilities to predict and manage the spread of flames. Firefighters base their actions on interacting forms of experiential and institutional knowledge, but shifting environmental conditions driven by climate change are disrupting the material, sensuous baselines upon which this knowledge is built. Aligning with STS research demonstrating that embodied senses are culturally produced, this paper analyzes how firefighters form environmental knowledge, predict fire behavior, and manage fire in volatile conditions. Drawing from ethnographic fieldwork, this paper shows this is a process in which firefighters learn to think, feel, and act towards ecologies in particular ways, to see landscapes as complex assemblages of hazardous things, the configuration of which signals a multitude of combustible potentialities. The formation of embodied fire knowledge, this paper shows, is a social process in which firefighters learn to see vegetation based on its flammability; to feel wind, humidity, and temperature to predict fire behavior; and to distinguish the smell of burning wood within charred forests. This area of research is under-examined, as much of the discourse revolves around techno-fixes such as drones, chemical fire suppressants, and geoengineering. This paper contributes to STS by examining the social production of embodied senses. I argue that embodied knowledge remains a central technology for sensing fire ecologies that are changing rapidly.

Playing along with the carpetbaggers, boondoggles and time-wasters in the search for a bushfire fix *Timothy Neale, Deakin University*

Southern Australia is one of the world’s worst areas for intense landscape fires, and for several number decades the management

of its temperate and highly flammable forests and grasslands have been the almost exclusive domain of large public land and fire agencies. Institutionally, these agencies have been preserved from some of the trends that have reshaped the wider public service, and similar public services internationally, in that: their employees are often “lifers”; they are frequently audited but have few clear quantitative markers of success; and, their budgets have grown in recent decades. Technologically, these agencies are also arguably unusual, in that the many tasks of detecting, analysing and predicting combustible environments tend to occur without shared standards, using some mix of bespoke regional infrastructures and free global ones. Following the landmark 2019-2020 “Black Summer” fires, which affected over 12 million hectares of southeast Australia, a number of enterprising companies have attempted to step in and “disrupt” this sedimented socio-technical system with “new” remote sensing and machine-learning technologies. In this paper, I will reflect on fieldwork amongst fire risk analysts within land and fire management agencies, their responses to such encounters with “carpetbaggers”, “boondoggles”, and “time-wasters” offering technical solutions, and how the reception of these alleged “fixes” reveal political contests within these agencies regarding their role in an increasingly flammable world.

Re-constituting the Sensory Infrastructures of Smart Forests
Jennifer Gabrys, University of Cambridge

Forests are increasingly sensorized environments. Whether in the form of camera traps to monitor organisms or Internet of Things to detect wildfires, there are an array of sensor technologies that observe and constitute forests in relation to scientific inquiry, Indigenous land claims, environmental governance, and disaster prevention and mitigation. This presentation will investigate the sensory arrangements that Smart Forests generate. It will ask how sensory infrastructures materialize as distributions of power and governance, while considering the sensory practices that transform and potentially re-constitute dominant regimes of perception.

Digital environmental governance regimes: The case of ‘smart’ fisheries on the US West Coast
Lauren Drakopoulos, Department of Geography, University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill

Digital surveillance technologies, such as cameras and satellite tracking systems, are transforming ocean governance. Heralded for making knowable otherwise unseen ocean environments, comparatively little is known about the ecologies and economies of ocean surveillance and data. In this talk, I draw on empirical data from a multi-sited ethnographic study of a digital fisheries monitoring program in the US to examine the emerging (digital) political ecologies of ocean surveillance. Although making fisheries ‘smart’ is argued to modernize ocean data and management, instead smart technologies introduce ontological, empirical, managerial, and technical concerns that are beyond the capacities of current environmental management frameworks to handle. Despite claims to bring greater transparency to extractive ocean industries, the complex data ecosystems of surveillance technologies have, in practice, proven opaque. To make sense of these contradictions, I develop the conceptual framework of digital environmental governance regime. Rather than fisheries surveillance programs evolving to meet management needs, governance frameworks are being reconfigured through new actors and power relations. I theorize the shift to digital environmental governance within the broader context of surveillance capitalism and question the implications for environmental data.

Session Organizers:

Alex Zahara, Department of Geography, Memorial University
Will Smith, Deakin University

Chair:

Timothy Neale, Deakin University

414. Toxic Entanglements: acting on slow, invisible, and emerging realities - III: Making Toxicity Visible

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

Chemical Traces: Towards a Relational Anthropology of Chemical Environments
Kim Hendrickx, Centre for Sociological Research, KU Leuven

Concerns about human health and the environment are leading to an increasing number of human biomonitoring (HBM) projects. HBM mobilizes cohorts of human volunteers to give samples (e.g. blood, milk, hair or urine) which are analyzed to identify traces of environmental pollutants. My project proposes an ethnography to analyze how pollutants are measured locally, and turned into ‘evidence’ informing future courses of action by policymakers and/or citizens. My ethnography focuses on empirical questions relating the technical sphere (methods and timeframes used to measure and define ‘exposure’), to social questions as to who is affected by pollution and whose voices are heard. I introduce the conceptual framework of the ‘chemical trace’ that guides my empirical work and its theorization. In the process from index to evidence, HBM measurements become chemical traces that reconnect past, present and future in order to become socially and politically actionable. In addition, biomonitoring is about the relations between our bodies and their environments: how do measurements and the construction presuppose and produce ontologies? Living in chemical environments is a cosmopolitical challenge at the junction of ontologies and timescapes.

Enclosed and Permeating Exposure
Elizabeth Roberts, University of Michigan

The scientists conducting a longitudinal environmental health study in Mexico City and their research subjects experience exposure differently. The scientists seek to understand the developmental effects of various chemicals like lead, BPA and fluoride over the long term. Their knowledge works to establish the damage of chemicals as they breach individual bodily boundaries. The scientists assume that bodies can somehow be cordoned off, enclosed from a world now saturated with harm. The study participants – mostly residents of working class neighborhoods, where heavy to light industry is common - don’t imagine enclosure as possible. They assume ceaseless permeating exposure to and with their surroundings. Assuming permeation makes it necessary to engage in a constant and capacious grappling with how exposure affects all of their relationships, not only their individual bodies. Through, their attunement to a wider set of relations, these working class residents of Mexico City provide alternative models for first, grapple with, then mitigating what damages life worlds today.

Learning to Touch Toxicity: How to Know and Care for Chemically Entangled Ecologies
Mayra Sanchez, University of California - Davis

Despite vast scientific evidence of risk exposure to many toxic chemicals such as synthetic pesticides, their often subtle, yet debilitating, noxious effects frequently remain unknown and invisible to those most vulnerable. This paper focuses on how activists and educators make sense of scientific findings and collectively craft more intimate ways of knowing that render more perceptible the pervasiveness of agroindustrial pesticides among those who work and live nearby California’s heavily polluted agricultural regions. Interweaving feminist theory, science and technology studies, and geographies of touch, it draws from ethnographic research to explore pedagogical encounters where participants learn to see and feel the presence of these technologies in their everyday lives in order to reduce future exposures. I suggest that by engaging with neglected senses and marginalized embodied experiences, the workings of

technoscience can become more visible and tangible, and thus, intervenable. Doing so, I highlight how a haptic epistemology may offer more tactful ways to attend, approach, and make sense of what it is like living among chemically-entangled relations. Contributing to a more careful politics of co-producing knowledge, this paper shows the power (and limits) of touch in helping generate care as well as responsibility against the slow techno-violence of our evermore toxic worlds.

What Counts as Toxic? Enactments of Chemical Exposure in a Human Biomonitoring Study and the Daily Lives of Agricultural Workers *Nolwenn Bühler, STS Lab, University of Lausanne*

Biochemicals permeate human bodies and blur their ontological boundaries by recalling their deep interconnectedness with other species and their environment. Their circulation is invisible and yet they operate in the depth of biologies and may affect health. How is biochemical exposure made visible? How does it come to matter? This paper tackles these questions by exploring enactments of biochemical exposure and questioning what counts as toxic in two different settings in Switzerland. The first is a biomonitoring study part of a public health population cohort. The study aims at making visible exposure by collecting large sets of data and biological samples. Enacting statistical and molecular understandings of exposure, it is embedded in an epistemic ideal in which the complexity of biochemical alterlives, their chronic and low-dose presence, might become calculable and knowable, with the prospect of developing evidence-based public health interventions. The second focuses on the daily experience of working with pesticides and other phytosanitary products in the agricultural community. Having to manipulate biochemicals for professional reasons they are led to negotiate and navigate various forms of toxic risks for themselves and others. Based on an ethnography of the biomonitoring project, interviews with scientists and public health experts, as well as with agricultural professionals, I will document the practical, epistemological and political challenges and frictions faced by these actors in making toxic realities count. I will also reflect on my own engagement as an anthropologist embarked in interdisciplinary collaboration to question the differential values granted to these toxic realities.

The Toxin Is (Not) The Mould – Confronting Invisible Toxicity On Farms In Upper Meru, Kenya *Konstantin Biehl Biehl, University of Oslo*

Establishing evidence of harmful impacts of chemicals introduced in agricultural production by human, or in the case of this paper, non-human actors takes a significant amount of time, resources, and techno-scientific know-how. However, it is seldom the end for the process of producing food considered safe. This paper addresses the re-translation of scientific knowledge on toxicity in the local context of farming in rural Kenya. Aflatoxins, a group of mycotoxins, produced by certain strains of mould are prevalent in soils and on plants all over the tropics. While an acute overdose can kill, long-term, low-dosage exposure significantly increases the risk of liver cancer. The slow and long-lasting impact on human and animal health as well as the invisible, odourless, and tasteless materiality of the toxins renders it almost impossible for farmers to directly address the problem while techno-scientific testing is largely absent from their villages. Based on participant observation in upper Meru, central Kenya, the paper describes how partially flawed knowledge about the dangers of and the lack of direct access to Aflatoxins is interwoven. It structures the farmer's engagement with mould, maize and concentrates food safety practices on mould rather than invisible toxins. This shift makes toxicity manageable but at the same times obscures the risk of exposure as mould and aflatoxins can exist materially separate. By closely following the farmers practices of separating mould and maize through the production cycle, the paper investigates lay people's

encounters and handling of invisible toxicity, practices of evaluation and the role of re-translated scientific knowledge in a local context.

Translating and transforming toxicity: moving from ethnography to graphic art *Amelia Fiske, Technical University Munich*

One of the principal means through which outsiders have come to recognize oil contamination in the Ecuadorian Amazon is through “Toxic Tours” in which a guide brings students, lawyers, environmental activists, journalists, and foreign tourists to visit toxic sites. Inspired by the creative ways that guides engage participants – inviting them to smell crude oil or to step out onto logs suspended over 3 meters of crude waste – the graphic novel *Tóxico* (University of Toronto Press 2022) immerses readers in the materiality of toxic contamination and struggles for environmental justice in everyday life. Based on ethnographic research conducted by the author between 2011-2013, the novel narrates the discovery of crude oil in waste pits and the stories of Ecuadorian interlocutors of living alongside industry through the journey of three participants on a “toxic tour.” Drawing on the experience of co-creating *Tóxico*, this paper explores the process of bringing graphic art and ethnography together in order to render toxicity in graphic form: What challenges emerge in moving from the partial, shifting, entangled knowledge of toxicity that emerges in the ethnographic encounter to graphic art? How is toxicity translated, and transformed, through the graphic form? Inspired by the urgency of life in a moment where preventing permeation by the continual, residual, overwhelming onslaught of industrial toxicants is neither possible nor expected, this paper explores the implications of conveying the sensory experiences of toxicity visually, and what this might mean for the ethnographic method in return.

Session Organizer:

Anita Hardon

415. Engaging Science, Technology, and Society (ESTS):

Editorial Board Meeting

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Editorial Board meeting for the 4S's Open Access journal, Engaging Science Technology, and Society.

Session Organizers:

Grant Jun Otsuki, Victoria University of Wellington

Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine

Alison Kenner, Drexel University

Emily York, James Madison University

Sujatha Raman, The Australian National University

Noela Invernizzi, Universidade Federal do Parana

Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University

Amanda Windle, Managing Editor, ESTS

Chair:

Aalok Khandekar, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad

416. Digital (Un)wellness: Power, Health, and Screen Time - IV

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Participants:

‘Are You There?’: The Interpersonal Challenges Overlooked by Smartphone Wellness Discourses *Kate Mannell, RMIT University*

Smartphones have been a key focus for popular and academic discussions about digital wellness. Typically, popular discourses focus on the device as a site of distraction, compulsion, and even addiction, while academic studies focus on people's attempts to curb device use in response to these and other concerns (e.g. Ribak & Rosenthal, 2015). In this paper, I highlight how one

particular smartphone function — mobile messaging — complicates people’s attempts to manage their smartphone use in ways that are yet to be fully acknowledged in either discussion. Drawing on interviews with young adults, I argue that there are specific socio-technical conditions that make messaging a uniquely complicated site for enacting practices of technology resistance and disconnection. Most significantly, messaging is a personal and often intimate form of communication that is also bound up in expectations of synchronous interaction and continual availability. This means that regulating messaging availability has significant relational implications as acts of disconnection do not just involve the device or platform, but also specific interlocutors who may be expecting a response. Building on this argument, I explain that while existing literature has highlighted that being able to disconnect is often a privilege (Portwood-Stacer, 2013), it is important to consider the specific equity issues that arise in the context of mobile messaging. Factors like gender and social capital can complicate people’s efforts to manage their smartphone use, while digital wellness discourses make assumptions about social connectedness that do not represent the experiences of those who are socially isolated.

Defining “Digital Well-being:” Conceptualizations of Healthy Technology Use at Social Platform Companies *Kellie Owens, University of Pennsylvania; Amanda Lenhart, Data & Society Research Institute*

For years, social media platforms basked in a glow of consumer and funder excitement, rapid growth, and positive press coverage. But recently, as these platforms have become more ubiquitous and powerful, the warm feelings have faded. One point of concern is the potential negative health effects of our increasing reliance on these platforms. What is all this time spent online doing to our mental and physical health? To explore these potential impacts, researchers and technologists developed the concept of “digital well-being.” One of the key problems with trying to improve digital well-being for users is that defining what counts as healthy or unhealthy technology use remains controversial—one person’s problematic, time-consuming internet use is another person’s organizing for a social justice movement or finding a support group. To better understand how digital well-being is being conceptualized and put into practice, we interviewed 25 current and former workers from a range of social media and social gaming platforms. Our respondents reported that there is little consensus about what counts as healthy technology use or digital well-being within their workplaces, and that companies are struggling to integrate these concepts into their product design processes. Often, companies rely on over-simplified frameworks like technology addiction because they can be easily measured through metrics like screen time. Or, they focus on their imagined “average” user, ignoring important subgroups. Our research analyzes these different approaches to “digital well-being” within social platforms companies, and provides recommendations for how these companies could improve their approaches.

Disconnection as a Digital Skill: Youth and Digital “Detoxing” *Michelle Gorea*

When using social media platforms, many young people possess the skill to navigate the platform, change platform privacy settings, use coded language to navigate across diverse actors and audiences, and selectively share information to keep their ‘private’ information private. However, for many young people, the use of digital devices is a significant source of anxiety, and many do not possess the necessary skills to disconnect, “detox”, or “cleanse” from the digital devices and digital practices associated with anxiety. Using a relational methodological approach that does not prioritize singular images but pays attention to the ways that the larger ‘media manifold’ fosters practices that are both directly and indirectly related to media, this paper examines how young people’s practices of digital disconnection can be conceptualized as a digital skill that many

are excluded from as a result of digital inequality across Generation Z. Drawing on in-depth interviews with 35 youth between the ages of 14-22, this paper outlines the multiple and complex ways that young people must navigate the normative frameworks surrounding digital technology use and disconnection. Findings indicate that many youths desire a need for more education and information surrounding realistic ways to disengage from social media use, either as a temporary “break” or as a longer-term lifestyle change. Given the pervasiveness of digital technologies in composing the texture of young people’s everyday lives, it is important to consider how the design of such technologies and their uses are multiply situated within a range of everyday contexts that may be positioned within practices of inequality.

Mutual Connections and Disconnections: Exploring the digital wellness practices of activists *Alex Beattie, Victoria University Wellington; Chad Valasek, University of California at San Diego*

This paper explores the digital wellbeing concerns and practices of political activists through interviews in the United States and New Zealand. In contrast to digital wellbeing approaches that individualize or pathologize technology use (i.e., Derks et al., 2021; Duke & Montag 2017), we posit a social model of digital wellbeing that focuses on the relations and activities between users and foregrounds the experiences of an underrepresented group in digital wellbeing studies. We explore how political activists practice on-screen/off-screen balance and investigate how the structure and culture of online organizing enables (or constrains) the integration of community care and self-care practices in organizer spaces. While digital wellbeing studies has become a resource for technology industries and wellness industries, less attention has been paid to how political activists conceive of digital wellbeing and what mutual care practices they might implement to support one another in instances of burnout or “screen fatigue.” Activists have a history of using communication devices to organize their political work, and the COVID-19 pandemic and consequent lockdowns have pushed more activists to use their digital devices as the main medium for coordination and political action. Moreover, with concerns over physical and mental “burnout,” we believe that activists are turning toward the support of their fellow organizers. Ultimately, we are interested in, and how activists’ digital wellness practices contrast to “therapeutic” institutional modes of digital wellbeing, such as corporate focused wellness or via digital wellness apps.

Session Organizers:

Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley
Alex Beattie, Victoria University Wellington
Laura Calloway, Indiana University
Chad Valasek, University of California at San Diego

Discussant:

Matthew Wolf-Meyer, Binghamton University

417. Good Governance, Good Relations and (Nuclear) Waste Management III

6:40 to 8:10 pm
4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Too often technical experts and government officials have seen the management and disposition of (nuclear) waste as a problem to be solved by experts, with the solution then “sold” to the broader public through techniques of public relations that are often so transparently manipulative as to be self-undermining. Instead of seeing waste management and disposition as narrowly technical problems to be resolved through techniques of quantitative risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis, they should be reframed as “wicked problems” (Churchman 1967, Rittel and Webber 1973) with the potential to disrupt good relations across a number of sociotechnical planes: between neighbors; between indigenous and settler populations; between corporations and local communities; between scientists and the public; and between state and society. Is it possible to

solve these problems without toxic social consequences? We call on colleagues to draw on STS and the knowledge of its multiple ancillary disciplines to imagine sociotechnical processes that could build good social, political, and environmental relations. This might involve critique of existing processes, reportage of innovative improvements, or advocacy of novel processes. It will surely involve multi-perspectival visioning. Our primary interest is in nuclear waste, but we will entertain proposed papers on other waste forms as well.

Participants:

End of engagement with deep time? Transformation of nuclear waste management from a collective concern into a market concern *Basak Saraç-Lesavre, The University of Manchester*

Since the abandonment of the long-planned and contested Yucca Mountain geological repository project in Nevada, in the United States, the national nuclear waste policy is in a state of deadlock. In the absence of an operational national nuclear waste program, and in the presence of an increasing number of reactors entering the decommissioning phase, with nothing but spent nuclear fuel to be stored at reactor sites, private industrial actors are seeking options to manage spent nuclear fuel on their own terms. This is well-illustrated by two licence applications for proposed private consolidated interim storage facilities pending before the Nuclear Regulatory Commission. This paper argues that spent nuclear fuel is increasingly subject to new forms of economic transactions based on new modalities of capitalism; assetisation and rentiership (Birch, 2017; Muniesa, 2017; Birch and Muniesa, 2020). The potential siting of these facilities raises a vital question: Does nuclear waste, once construed as a collective concern whose governance affects the present and future of American society with the potential to extend to hundreds of thousands of years, transform into a market concern? Empirically focusing on current developments, this paper analyses the transformation that the temporal orientation of 'responsible' action undergoes in the United States, and interrogates whether such a transformation signals an end of engagement with deep time and with attempts to construe 'desirable' and 'valuable' arrangements among temporally and spatially defined collectives (Saraç-Lesavre, 2020, 2021).

Make it Our Shared Wicked Problems! The "Pathways Evolution Process" Serious Game as Challenger for Radioactive Waste Management Strategies *Céline Parotte, University of Liege - Spiral; Nathan Flore, University of Liege; Florence Ciralo, University of Liege*

While STS scholars generally point out that radioactive waste management (RWM) is a sociotechnical issue, in practice the social and technical aspects are still assessed separately. At the European level, regulatory bodies and their technical support organizations are aware of this issue and are looking for innovative ways to address it. With the support of social experts, they recently created the "Pathways Evolution Process (PEP) Serious Game" dedicated to RWM. This foresight game initially aims at challenging RWM strategies and fostering interactions with civil society (SITEX project, 2021). Concretely, the PEP Serious Game creates and imposes shared wicked problems that participants must solve together within a specific timeframe. Based on document analysis, semi-structured interviews, participatory observations and ethnographic fieldnotes, this presentation compares two recent national experiences of the PEP Serious Game applied to RWM in France (2019) and Belgium (2021). Both participatory exercises were designed to target young participants with multidisciplinary background and were jointly organized by technical and social experts, with the support of French and Belgian nuclear regulatory bodies and their technical support organizations. Our results highlight how this tool creates, perpetuates or temporarily challenges relationships between technical and social experts (from universities and relevant public administrations) and stakeholders of the future generation. A central question we ask is: what if

playing seriously was a way to collectively challenge nuclear waste policies?

Nuclear Waste Futures and the Limits of Representation *William Kinsella, North Carolina State University*

This paper considers problems of temporality, complexity, and institutional control related to the storage and disposition of high-level nuclear wastes. The paper draws upon an established body of scholarship in STS, temporalities studies, sociologies of risk, social systems theory, and communication studies. I extend a framework addressing the limits of representation, both epistemic and political, in prevailing nuclear waste discourses. In the epistemic domain, approaches based on calculative modeling, risk assessment, and prediction are inevitably fraught with limitations. Systemic complexity and extended temporality magnify the consequences of those epistemic limitations over nuclear wastes' multi-millennial timescales. In the political domain the limits of representation are twofold: modeling systems of nuclear waste governance requires imagining far-distant social, political, and cultural futures; and the political representation of far-future stakeholders involves challenges in imagining their characteristics, needs, rights, and interests. While conducting ethnographic fieldwork in 2012, the author was struck by a comment made by a high-level U.S. government official, who stated that he could not imagine a scenario in which the government would fail to dispose of existing nuclear wastes in time to prevent damaging consequences. Nine years later the U.S. appears no closer to a solution, while a global pandemic, economic stresses, severe political division, and the January 2021 attack on the U.S. Capitol suggest that long-term institutional control of nuclear wastes may be less certain than that official suggested. Accordingly, after examining the representational problems at stake, the paper develops suggestions for expanding the vision of nuclear waste discourse and governance.

"We Write The Final Chapter Together" Nuclear Waste Management In Germany - The Role Of Science *Sarah Glück, Federal Office for the Safety of Nuclear Waste Management; Zoe Felder, Federal Office for the Safety of Nuclear Waste Management; Ina Richter, Federal Office for the Safety of Nuclear Waste Management; Christoph Borkel, Federal Office for the Safety of Nuclear Waste Management*

Germany is facing the challenge to find a solution to safely deal with its high radioactive wastes. The debate took off with the final agreement of nuclear phase-out of 2011 and the proclamation of the Site Selection Act (StandAG, 2017). The Act defines a wide ranging participation of the public during the search process as part of a participatory, science-based, transparent, self-reflective and learning process (StandAG § 1). Formal and informal actors from science, society, and the political as well as administrative parts of the state are bound by manifold relations and processes that happen simultaneously. Among the actors the Federal Office for the Safety of Nuclear Waste Management is directly confronted with questions such as: how will the relations between scientists and publics, between state and society and between the federal states of Germany develop throughout the search process? The long-term search process (exceeding a decade), is and will be confronted with foreseeable and unforeseeable sociotechnical developments. The paper uses the notion of energy epistemics (Miller et al 2013) to examine the German nuclear waste management debate and the role of the science division of the Federal Office for the Safety of Nuclear Waste Management within the search process.

Session Organizer:

Allison Macfarlane, George Washington University

Chair:

Allison Macfarlane, George Washington University

418. Knowing Platforms - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

Participants:

Knowing Platforms through Workers; Knowing Workers through Platforms *Rida Qadri, MIT*

In this paper I reflect on two divergent modes of knowing the platform and the worker: a ground-up, worker-centered, ethnographic inquiry and a top-down, platform-centered, computational inquiry. From 2019-2020, I embedded myself within mobility platform driver communities in Jakarta, intimately following their social relationships, technologies of work and everyday acts of resistance. I knew the platform only as the drivers knew it. In 2020, I acquired a different vantage point when I became part of Uber as a research data scientist. As I metaphorically entered the platform drivers became dots on a map--I knew them only as the platform knew them. Through this paper I make sense of these contradictory research positionalities. What epistemologies undergirded each inquiry, what relationships were illuminated and what realities were obscured? What methodological, social and political choices were made in both cases? A comparative reflection allows me to comment on how researchers of platforms can capture the shifting realities and multifarious relationships that a platform embodies. My experience also is a reminder that as researchers we must be cognizant of our own position in relation to the platform as the lens adopted can re-configure what is seen of the platform and of the worker.

Knowing through undoing: Creative, collaborative, and disruptive strategies for unmaking public knowledge about crowdfunding platforms *Nora Kenworthy, University of Washington - Bothell; Jin-Kyu Jung, University of Washington Bothell*

What should researchers do when what is 'knowable' about platformed data, even after exhaustive investigative efforts, does not reflect actual user experiences? After years of intensive ethnographic, quantitative and geospatial efforts to understand the experiences of people using GoFundMe, we have had to reckon with several persistent challenges that limit what is knowable from crowdfunding data. In addition to being filtered by platform and cross-platform algorithms, crowdfunding data is heavily shaped by cultural scripts and platform affordances that influence how users tell and share stories. Platformed, public stories constitute data full of occlusions and silences. We introduce a nascent project that reconstitutes and disrupts this platformed data, using undoing and remaking as strategies for alternative ways of knowing. Borrowing techniques from digital humanities, we envision an interactive web interface of non-linear 'storyscapes' that disrupt the affects, narratives and ontologies of crowdfunding platforms, creating transformative ontogenetic spaces for new affective engagements, knowledges, and narratives to emerge. We creatively recombine existing ethnographic and quantitative data, geovisualizations, and participatory narratives to produce storyscapes such as: emplaced poems created from composite campaign narratives alongside ethnographic data; affective geovisualizations of crowdfunder experiences, and reconstituted imagery of crowdfunding pages embedded with "metadata" on the hidden structural factors shaping campaign outcomes. With these efforts, we seek to create an alternative 'platform' for collaboratively making what is invisible in crowdfunding visible and sensory, engaging the public in the creation of counter-narratives about what crowdfunding is, and what it affords, in the context of deep structural inequities.

Knowing your app: socio-technical entanglements of apps for migrants *Olga Usachova, University of Padova*

The so-called "long summer of migration" (Römhild et al., 2018) in Europe in 2015-2016 not only uncovered the "messy networks" (Bijker & Law, 1992, p. 12) of migrant reception

infrastructures but also imposed a challenge to the hosting society to re-think and adjust the ways how the acceptance and further social integration process functions. Following the rapid development and employment of the digital tools in migration governance, to respond to this challenge the massive development of digital platforms and mobile applications for migrants took place. This study aims at reflecting on the practices of knowing the migrant apps by different migrant groups present in Germany and what is the relation between knowing and the use of migrant apps. Drawing on ethnographic work in Germany, we employed the "following the app" method which brought the possibility to find the app users and understand the usage patterns and motivation behind it. Therefore, in this paper, we argue that the gap between knowing and using migrant apps has its impact on the sustainability of the digital initiatives. Moreover, the driving forces of use of the mobile application for migrants, such as locality of the presented information, the possibility of instant interaction, up-to-date content, are the prerequisites to take a step further from knowing to using of mobile application.

"Multi-Sited" Markets: A relational approach to studying platformed social life *Julia Ticona Ticona, University of Pennsylvania, Annenberg School for Communication*

Platforms are understood as "walled gardens," enclosing social relations to extract profit. But, even if this metaphor is an accurate way of understanding their business practices, it provides a poor model through which to study their social lives. Often defined as "multi-sided markets," platforms narrate their services to many stakeholders, including consumers, workers, advertisers, and regulators, and reshape social relations across disparate contexts. However, studies of working alongside platforms have mostly examined workers' relationships to algorithms, and ethnographers often confine themselves to interactions that occur within the "garden walls". Taking a relational approach to platforms as an ethnographic object, this paper will offer methodological reflections on tracing the social life of carework platforms. I offer that we can trace these social lives by attending to 1) links, 2) leaks, and 3) layers. Platforms are socio-technical systems that bind different social actors into relations with one another. Borrowing from economic sociology, we can seek out the ways that different social actors are linked through the cultural construction of rules, norms, and scripts for economic exchange. Drawing on multi-site and networked ethnographies, we can look for the places where platform exchanges "leak" out into other contexts. Finally, the political economy and history of platforms and their markets are crucial to understanding the contingency of ethnographic observations in the present. These layers are inseparable from our understandings of platform power and the social inequalities that attend the social lives of platforms.

Session Organizer:

Moira Weigel, Northeastern University

419. Art, Science and Technology Studies - V: Multidisciplinary Histories in Art and Science

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Chair: Chris Salter

Participants:

Thinking in pictures: Methodological reflections on a dialogue of sociology and visual arts *Marie-Kristin Doebler, Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nuernberg; Heta Tarkkala, University of Eastern Finland; Annerose Boehler, Friedrich-Alexander University Erlangen-Nuernberg; Susi Vetter, Self employed*

Collaborating with illustrators has a long tradition in medicine or natural sciences, but is still rather uncommon in social sciences. So far social sciences primarily turn towards visuals when art is

their field of research, drawings/photographs/footage their data or graphs/figures the mode of presenting results. However, we just start to discover alliances with professional illustrators. In our project 'Faces of Masking' we are trying to overcome this gap between art and social sciences. Besides investigating masking practices and narratives during Covid-19 pandemic we explore alternative formats of presenting, but especially of gaining scientific insights. The artist's sketches are part of the analytical process adding new layers to the scientific interpretation resulting in an art-science ping-pong: illustrations are interwoven with the analysis, embedded in the scientific-methodological reflections and the writing process, and used for presenting the findings. Intended as exploration of qualitative methodologies our experience sheds light on several issues: contrary to the well-known graphs and figures, more creative visuals tend to get questioned in terms of aesthetics and themselves challenge traditional disciplinary differentiations. Although, reactions to our work have been mostly very positive, their use needs to be explained and justified much more than standardised forms of visuals. Additionally, there is a lack of infrastructures and institutions enabling for artists and sciences coappearance. Conferences, awards or publications mostly fit for one, not for both parties in such liaisons. Thus, we would happily cease the chance offered by this panel for reflecting on our collaborative work and sharing the lessons-learned.

Material Relations In The Classroom: Orra White Hitchcock's Geologic Charts *Allison Fulton, Dept of English / STS at UC Davis*

Scientific artist Orra White Hitchcock created dozens of hand-painted canvas charts and diagrams to be used as lecture aids in her husband Edward Hitchcock's geology classrooms at Amherst College. In published and personal accounts of Orra and Edward's working relationship, Orra is described as both a scientific affiliate and a scientific instrument. On the one hand, as Edward's laboring affiliate, Orra is lauded for visually rendering his theories accessible; on the other, as a scientific instrument, Orra becomes a literal extension of Edward's body, her hand tracing the earth's strata only at his will. The charts that she produced in this dual role consolidate facts into manageable systemic arrangements and thus were crucial for defining student success in the classroom. I argue that to understand the theoretical developments in the early disciplinary history of American geology, we must attend to Orra and her classroom charts as vital components of Edward's student-teacher relationships. I do so by highlighting where and when Orra's artistically-skilled body, in tandem with her scientific illustrations, is invoked and implemented as a pedagogical tool. But to more accurately account for how Orra and her charts functioned as scientific instruments, I contend that we must also consider specifics of how the visualizations were brought to form through embodied and laborious practice. More broadly, this paper posits that it is crucial to reconsider historical moments where major scientific concepts were taught through visual form to reckon with the ways contemporary scientific practice is visually materialized.

Qatipana: Towards the possibility of Cosmotronics and Technodiversity *Renzo Christian Filinich, Universidad de Valparaiso*

This essay revolves around the concepts and processes of Becoming and Individuation where a functional model based on the articulation of an information processing system based on the approaches of the philosopher Gilbert Simondon is evidenced; This research aims to observe a sensorimotor cycle performed by the cognitive system of an Artificial Intelligence agent. To establish this model of biological inspiration, we used the concepts of information and modulation in Gilbert Simondon and information in cybernetics of Norbert Wiener and Stafford Beer. These resources force us to ask ourselves the following question: How does mono-technology and computerization of cultural

techniques influence the very nature of knowing the affect of being with others (people, things, animals)? To answer this question, an interdisciplinary study (arts, sciences, information technologies) is offered on the effect of this symbiosis and how it can be seen in the full use of knowledge about the fundamentals of living and non-living matter. The architecture is called Qatipana (a Quechua word that denotes the flow of information processing systems), although it cannot be considered as a systems theory, it has the utility of being able to explain some empirical observations that are presented here. In conclusion, the implications and limitations of this model and the research that is being carried out to present its utility and probability as a technodiversified model of the algorithmic cognitive system are part of the issues of communication and affect in the decisions that this cybernetic system provides.

'Reconfiguring the Remainder'? – Robot Design, Adversarial Play, and Critical Aesthetics *Philippe Sormani, University of Lausanne*

Carl DiSalvo's (2012) Adversarial Design pursues a critical and arguably constructive motive. Its critical motive emphasizes contentious design and agonistic encounter, enabling disagreement and frame subversion, as a conspicuous challenge to the consensual surfaces of 'design for politics' (e.g., PR) and its 'techniques of merging form and content in aesthetically compelling and functionally appropriate ways to support the means of governance' (p. 8). Drawing upon a video ethnography of robot design, this paper pauses on the 'arguably constructive motive' of Adversarial Design, namely its design motive aiming at 'reconfiguring the remainder' (chap. 3). Drawing upon both Suchman (2006) and Honig (1993), DiSalvo defines this move and motive as an 'agonistic tactic of including what is commonly excluded, giving it privilege, and making it the dominant character of the designed thing' (p. 64). In turn, the present paper challenges this design motive for its questionable construction, as the motive's 'inclusive corrective' takes for granted the exclusionary frame, if tactically so. To make its case, the paper presents a video analysis of adversarial play with so-called 'educational robots,' play that not only subverted a given frame (e.g., 'AI'), but also instituted new games, if not a disjunctive différend (Lyotard 1984). In other words, the paper takes a particular interest in how the involved players, school kids and robot ethnographers, re- and co-design a 'critical aesthetics' on the fly.

Session Organizer:

Chris Salter, Concordia University

420. The Race to Digitalization and its attendant consequence of inequality - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

The global economy is experiencing increased digital transformation with its impacts felt globally and in all economic sectors. Digitalization enhances productivity with increased impacts on e-governance, telemedicine, distant learning, market access, remote-working, manufacturing etc. Digital technological capabilities however, remain concentrated in technological advanced economies and the digital economy is creating emerging new forms of inequality and wider technological gaps. The rise in digitization has reshaped markets, the world of business and work, raising inequalities within economies and distorting income distribution. The distribution of both capital and labor income has become more unequal, with income largely shifting from labor to capital. Developing countries (especially those in African) will not easily finance digitalization due to the high cost of infrastructure to develop and support robotics, automation and other digital technologies. The disruptions caused by COVID-19 pandemic have increased the need for digitalization and catch-up remains unattainable. New forms of nationalisms are growing, border closures and restrictions of movements of humans and goods are all in a bid to stop the spread of the virus. Digitalization is sure to increase if business transactions are to continue. This has made countries to develop

national digital policies. However, policy failures of past industrial policies may still hunt these countries. This panel will contribute to knowledge on how to structure digitalization that will enhance the attainment of sustainable development to reduce inequality and technological divide. We are also seeking to understand the likely factors causing the digital divide and national policies to regulate the impacts digitalization in developing countries. Potential topics include: Digitalization, digital technologies, inequalities, developing countries, digital policies

Participants:

Race-ing To The Digital: Blackness As Interruption in Technological Systems *Daniel Meyerend, University of Michigan*

Is the notion of classification inherently a white enterprise? And if so, how then is Blackness understood as a part of this enterprise? My project seeks to examine how images of Blackness intersect with classification systems within digital technologies. There is a lineage in Black Studies that names Blackness as a constant interruption and disruption in the ongoing project of constructing “the human”, and my project examines this phenomenon as Blackness comes into contact with new digital platforms and technologies. More specifically, I examine the case study of an AI dataset where models were able to generate high resolution images from a low resolution input image that are perpetually realistic and downscale correctly. At the surface, this technology is seemingly helpful and even groundbreaking, but a problem arose when a low resolution image of Barack Obama was given and the image generated was a white Obama. Yann LeCun, a senior VP at Facebook claimed that this was merely an issue of the network being trained on a dataset that contained pictures of white people, but Timnit Gebru, an AI analyst for Google, pushed back against the notion that harms can be reduced to dataset bias, calling for more critical understandings of how racism can be embedded within these systems. My paper utilizes a critical cultural approach to the Internet, grounded in Critical Technocultural Discourse Analysis (CTDA) to examine not only the AI dataset, but the larger conversation around this moment on digital platforms.

Infrastructuring Peace and the Promises of Information Information *Caroline Mason, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute - STS*

From H.G Well and JCR Licklider to Vannevar Bush and Paul Otlet, the possibilities of ‘libraries of the future’ have long been imagined in science fiction literature, prophesized by technologists, and pursued by various corporate and governmental bodies. Imagined as decentralized, universal, and neutral information storage and retrieval systems, what Well’s World Brain and Otlet’s Memorandum share in common lies not just in their similar visions of technological advancement and progress but also in their shared visions of social progress. Rooted in the intellectual traditions of utopianism and positivism, these imaginaries of global information infrastructures all shared the same utopian goal – world peace. Although the technology through which such visions were expressed was quickly superseded by digital computing technology, the utopian imaginaries surrounding the digitalization of libraries persist. The World Digital Library (WDL), a joint venture by the Library of Congress and UNESCO to preserve, curate, and provide access to “the world’s most important cultural treasures”, shares the familiar objective of fostering “international understanding”, ‘building knowledge society’, and ‘bridging the digital divide’. However, since its inception, the WDL has been met with backlash for participating in cultural and digital imperialism, particularly from librarians in the Global South. Situating the WDL in its historical context, my talk will examine the nuances between the WDLs imagined intent and its political, economic, and cultural impact, focusing on international power relations, policies, information extraction, and inequality. My talk will conclude with suggestions for the structuring of more just digital

libraries.

National policies for curbing digital inequalities *Emmanuel Ejim-Eze, Institute of Engineering, technology and innovation Management; Deborah Ogochukwu Ejim-Eze, Foundation for Sustainability Science in Africa/ Obafemi Awolowo University, Ile-Ife*

Prior to COVID19 pandemic, the world was making some progress towards the attainment of sustainable development goals (even this progress was uneven), but it was not certainly on track to meet the goals. The progress made in reducing poverty, hunger, infant and maternal mortality rates, HIV/AIDs, malaria and other infectious disease seem to be serious reversed. The world now witness lack of access to health care, literacy programmes, fewer sources of income, lack of access and other public services. Various regulations limiting physical human interactions while enforcing social distant rules would have being benign with the use of digital technologies to bridge gaps. Lack of these digital technologies increase inequality and access to public services. Factors increasing digital divided especially in developing countries include low digital readiness of countries in terms of having poorer customs, trade facilitation, logistics, absorptive capacity and skills. Some big techs have gotten richer and have extended their markets to developing countries who lack digital infrastructure. Several local firms have lost the market due to the impacts of covid-19 pandemic. This has also gone ahead with loss of local employment and income. These local economies do not have any barrier to stop the entrance of foreign big techs. Countries in developing world do not have options than to introduce industrial policies that will regulate digitalization and reduce inequality of their citizenry. The paper is looking at kinds of policies that could help regulate digitalization in developing countries while enhancing telemedicine, literacy programmes, market access, remote-jobs .et.c

Session Organizer:

Emmanuel Ejim-Eze, Institute of Engineering, technology and innovation Management

421. Thinking the Limits: AI Ethics/AI Unbound II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

In what way might it be productively disruptive to think through the “limits” of AI. Implicitly, we find in the call for an ethical AI or an unbiased or fair AI a condition of a limit. Advanced automation may have a place in a post-industrial military-industrial complex, but that should not be in the form of a military “killer robot.” Algorithmic sorting can effectively produce types and categories, but that sorting should not reproduce a racist logic. And yet, the empirical difficulty of distinguishing the method and trajectory of the automated outcome—the black box state of current deep learning—broadly impacts the application of AI technology from the quotidian to the exceptional event. This panel discusses the idea of a “limit” to AI across several critical paradigms, including a feminist/queer technoscience ethical right of refusal, a critical race theory framing of eugenic programming and unbounded fugitive technologies, as well as geolocal political economies of AI industry including labor and environment.

Participants:

AI Ethic's Epistemic Failures for Racial Justice *Rashida Richardson, Visiting Scholar, Rutgers Law School*

This talk examines the need for epistemic reforms of AI ethics discourse and interventions regarding algorithmic bias and racial inequities. While popular media and academic outlets have recognized how the lack of diversity in the technology and academic sectors contribute to algorithmic bias, less attention is given to how the lack of diversity constrains and distorts conceptualizations of the “algorithmic bias problem” and potential solutions. Focusing on the US AI sector in particular, I ask how does the compounded effects of hypersegregation in

United States impact key questions regarding AI's role in society including, what societal issues AI is developed to address, how we evaluate AI's potential and consequences, and what interventions can adequately mitigate AI's flaws. A brief review of the answers to these questions reveals the need for epistemic reform and I will conclude with a recommended framework that can enable substantive change in AI Ethics discourse.

Broken AI Still Makes Carceral Infrastructure: Unbinding from AI, Rebinding in Coalition *Lilly Irani, University of California, San Diego; Paul Khalid Alexander, San Diego City College*

In 2016, the City of San Diego installed 3,000 “smart streetlights” with the promise that the new infrastructure would save electricity, enable data-driven planning, and power an app-fueled innovation economy. City Council did not discuss the technology’s cameras, microphones, algorithms, or data ownership regimes. Five years later, the object detection AI never even properly worked and the City was left with thousands of cameras controlled by its police department. AI and the innovation economy was a broken promise, but a carceral infrastructure. We propose a holistic analysis of the San Diego Smart Streetlights program, the work of the coalition of technology workers, criminalized communities, and immigrant communities that came together to gain democratic oversight and control not only of this program, but all surveillance technologies acquired by the city. The coalition formed around an analysis of the streetlights not just through data privacy, but through a recognition of the potential of the technologies to exacerbate existing systems of oppression and exploitation such as gang suppression units and deportation regimes, as well the alienation of tech workers who did not want their extracted labor to contribute to such systems. The policy organizing allowed communities usually not in interaction to build coalition through mutual learning and grow their capacity to organize while extending existing racial justice coalitions to reform policing. Questions of ethical AI proved less relevant than a politics of refusal and coalition building. Racial capitalism’s roadmap for innovation moves through cities as sites of accumulation so surveillance oversight and transparency ordinances, carefully designed, can produce occasions for organizing, community education, and movement building while creating friction to resist projects of capital accumulation.

The limits of an AI ecosystem *Alessandra Renzi, Concordia University*

Montreal, QC has become Canada’s largest AI center, with tech giants as well as start-ups opening new offices in the city, the development of a federal AI supercluster, many R&D institutes and campuses, as well as considerable federal, provincial and municipal investment. The most prominent brains behind these efforts promote the notion of an ecosystem instead of that of an AI cluster. In their use, an AI ecosystem builds ties and connections among industries, sectors and governance rather than simply promote the specific attributes of a given cluster or hub. This paper explores the limits of AI by theoretically and empirically developing the notion of an AI ecosystem in relation to what Sara Safransky calls the “geographies of algorithmic violence” of racial capitalism. It focuses specifically on the case of gentrification and anti-gentrification struggles in Montreal’s neighborhoods adjacent to the AI industry headquarters, in order to interrogate the less visible impacts of AI on vulnerable groups and neighbourhoods. Finally the paper presents data resulting from ongoing community action research and housing justice organizing through the lenses of platform studies, STS and critical urban planning to highlight some of the AI ecosystem’s constituting components and processes of consolidation that movements of resistance could tackle.

Session Organizer:

Beth Coleman, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Meredith Broussard, associate professor at the Arthur L. Carter Journalism Institute of New York University

422. Becoming with Water: Ethnographic and Methodological Reconfigurations — V

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

This panel is an invitation to disrupt eurocentric ontologies of water. Simultaneously, the papers move with water to reorient us towards previously excluded indigenous, black and more than human epistemologies of water, waterways and watery spaces. Thinking with scholarship on new materialisms, decoloniality, critical pedagogies, the papers unmoor the temporalities that eurocentric modernities reify and take for granted. Instead, they draw attention to temporal possibilities that emerge from relearning our sensorial, affective, political and ethical ties to and with water. Through their work, the authors advance STS scholarship by deliberately and seriously engaging with water’s flows, stagnations, turbulences and pluripotency as theory.

Participants:

Broken Ocean *Stefan Helmreich, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)*

The ocean is not broken — not yet. But its breaking waves are full of breaking news, portents, perhaps, of what is to come. What happens when a wave breaks? A million things. It can sculpt or erode a beach. It can surge and seep into land, can fracture breakwater infrastructure. It may spume and spit sodium nitrate into the air if the ambient coastal atmosphere is dosed with nitrogen dioxide from car exhaust. In an age in which oceans are beset by fast and slow disaster — ongoing nuclear contamination, overfishing, acidification, plastification, and more — breaking waves are material forms that carry signs of old and new environmental violence and injustice. What Christina Sharpe, writing of “the transverse waves of the wake” of Atlantic slave ships, theorizes as “the wake” — “a region of disturbed flow” in which “the past that is not past appears, always, to rupture the present” — is therefore joined by the break, the unfurling edge of future disruption both inexorable and unpredictable. The “wake work” that Sharpe names in *In the Wake: On Blackness and Being* — critical work of mourning and living in the afterlife of slavery and global anti-Blackness — may thus be complemented by break work (a term I owe to Melody Jue), critical work to foresee and forestall climate and coastal transformation. Breaking waves may be read, too, as figures for breaking relations with those calamitous futures that have been prepared by the oceanic dispossessions of slavery, hydrocolonialism, and the militarization of sea space.

Thinking with Seafoam: More-than-Wet Engagements with Pebble Mine, Alaska *Katherine Ball, Arizona State University*

Pebble Partnership is a proposed mine on an expansive copper deposit in south-eastern Alaska where ocean turbulence continuously redefines the visible representation of the mine’s future. I explore Pebble Mine through an extension of Peters and Steinberg’s (2019) more-than-wet ontology. This ontology thinks from the ocean rather than from the land about the ocean. Seafoam extends the framework as a tool for understanding assemblages of material, social, and political actants as an aggregate made visible by turbulence within wet encounters. A more-than-wet seafoam approach to Pebble Mine enables thinking from the offshore to observe how ocean materialities exceed their physical properties and travel beyond customary ocean bounds in imagined futures. This project characterizes the instability of Pebble Mine as seafoam through an exploration of mine byproducts that were central to public narratives in 2015 as ocean materialities generated beyond the geographic boundaries of Bristol Bay. These byproducts engage in more-than-human relations with infrastructure, living things, and social practices

and extend the ocean outward as stabilizing actants within sea foams of imagined futures. The turbulence of social and political histories of the region and their ongoing tensions generate a multitude of sea foams within the more-than-human relations across Pebble Mine's narrative. The outcomes of this turbulence remains imagined as Pebble Mine is washed up in court over its environmental impact statement. Thinking with the assemblage of seafoam allows for continuous reconfigurations of Pebble Mine as it is carried in the making of new Alaska futures.

Exploring New Materialism Through Bobcaygeon's Lock 32
Christopher Rogers, University of Waterloo

Water enlivens and flows through us, yet is often labeled and imagined as a stagnant, unmoving mass. Globes, maps, and charts tell us where water is, help us understand its size, but not where it moves, how it feels, smells or tastes. The fluidity of water makes it difficult to grasp. Working from the perspective of a unified natureculture, thinking with our bodies and water provides a helpful perspective for examining how we interact with and conceive of watery spaces. This talk attends to how we can explore human-created watery spaces, or anthropohydrocosms (Saulnier-Talbot and Lavoie 2018), through place-based knowledge, and how we can work at being with water through a sensory ethnography approach. In examining human-created watery spaces in relation to existing new materialist thought, I investigate how these spaces offer us new ways of knowing. Examining Lock 32 in Bobcaygeon, Ontario, the first settler attempt to connect Lake Ontario with Lake Huron through the 386-kilometer inland Trent-Severn Waterway, this talk considers the enduring pain its construction has caused and continues to represent for Indigenous communities, and reflects on the ways new materialism might help us chart a path forward. In advocating for a situated approach attuned to senses, through Lock 32 we can observe the mixing of space, bodies, and things, and understand water as something more-than. Grounded in the notion of accountability, this talk asks practitioners in STS to consider careful and thoughtful methodological approaches to studying watery spaces.

Unsettling Water Pedagogies
Fikile Nxumalo, OISE, University of Toronto

In this paper, I discuss the potential of pedagogies that bring young people into reciprocal relationships with water. I draw from critical ethnographic and participatory work with young people and educators in everyday place-based encounters in the context of Central Texas. An important orientation of this work, both pedagogically and conceptually, is trying to figure out what it might look like to learn with place, and its more-than-human inhabitants, in ways that disrupt settler colonial and anti-Black inheritances. These inheritances include Eurowestern human exceptionalism which manifests in myriad ways in place-based education including a normalized understanding of the natural world as intrinsically separate from, and lesser than humans. This separation shows up for instance when nature is described in ways that construct it primarily as a mute site for young learners' meaning-making and their universalized cognitive, physical and socio-emotional developmental progression. I share three short stories of learning with water that individually and collectively illustrate decolonial ways of welcoming young people into relationship with the more-than-human. The stories are place stories, meaning that they inherently tethered to the places in which they are situated. Therefore, rather than offering them as practices to follow, I share these stories to highlight the ways in which they matter pedagogically as an ethos for living well with human and more-others within and beyond educational spaces. In particular I invite readers to think with water pedagogies of reciprocity, relationality and testifying-witnessing in relation to their necessity as an ethos for Black, Indigenous and Black-Indigenous futures.

Session Organizer:

Shweta Krishnan, George Washington University

Chair:

Dana Burton, George Washington University

423. Toward a Critical Health Informatics: Traversing Policy and Practice II - Cases and Explorations

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

This second session features works that centralize explorations in critical health informatics, such as case studies and applications.

Participants:

(Un)Controllable control: Public perceptions of blockchain in health care
Victoria Neumann, Lancaster University; Gail Davidge, University of Manchester

Health data management systems are often hierarchical, centralised models with public and private health organisations acting as primary data custodians and gatekeepers on behalf of patients and as intermediaries for third party data users. In the recent years, researchers have begun to explore the use of Distributed Ledger Technologies (DLT), also known as blockchain, in health care. Visions of decentralised forms of personal health data management and mechanisms to create interoperability within disparate health care systems are connected to promises of emancipating patients and giving them back control and possible incentives to share their own data. In this presentation, we highlight results from a co-design process and focus group research from an interdisciplinary project on blockchain uses in health care. In particular, we will present participants notions of control and power related to the core features of DLT. The results show a deconstruction of libertarian ideas to technically remove intermediary or central authorities by participants in favour of institutionalised control. Further, participants saw individual control as a mix of data self-protection measures and proactive strategies of participating and executing agency in health care systems. They were interested if DLT could enable them to gain greater participatory agency, but also voiced concerns it be used to limit these possibilities, deepen existing inequalities and it is not set up to ensure equitable access to services. Our research shows that social justice considerations need to be taken into account for designing personal health informatics systems for wide-scale adoption.

Harm Reduction for Health Internet of Things (IoT) Devices
Laura Calloway, Indiana University

As health and healthcare becomes more electronically mediated, it is critical for any associated privacy risks to be well understood. In addition, since technological and health risks are not distributed homogeneously, but rather experienced unequally due to the lived experiences and identities of users (as a result of their race/ethnicity, class, gender identity, sexual orientation, disability status, citizenship, or any combination thereof) it is critical to outline these risks as a function of what the most minoritized users are likely to experience. Reducing risks for the most marginalized means less risk for society as a whole. This work builds on previous research on risk perception expanding our understanding of risks and harms specific to the above minoritized groups within the added surveillance structures of the global Coronavirus pandemic. Harm reduction is a well-established approach to addressing how to navigate risk in higher risk situations, especially for health-related risks. Support for applying harm reduction strategies in a user driven way, with a focus on integrating the perspectives of affected individuals (and communities, continues to grow. This work focuses security and privacy evaluations of popular Internet of Things (IoT) devices whose primary purpose is not health related but may have auxiliary health functions or capabilities (i.e., a smart speaker listening for users coughing due to COVID-19) as well as internet connected health devices used both commercially (i.e., pulse oximeter) and in the home (i.e., fitness tracker) in order to

provide public policy recommendations for better protection of consumer privacy.

The Role of Search Engines in the Sexual Health Information Seeking of LGBTQ+ Youth *Daniel Delmonaco*

Introduction: LGBTQ+ youth rely on the internet as an information resource especially for sexual health information that they are often unable to receive elsewhere, including from healthcare professionals and in school settings. The role of algorithmic search engines is an understudied component of LGBTQ+ youth and their reliance on internet resources to meet sexual health information needs. Search engines and the algorithms that drive impact the sexual health information access of LGBTQ+ youth. In our findings, previous conceptions of search engines directly influenced search strategies, assessment of results, and thus understandings of one's own body.

Methods: In summer and fall 2020, I conducted 17 interviews with self-identified LGBTQ+ young people (15 to 25 years old) in the United States. Semi-structured interviews included questions about sexual health information seeking experiences of participants and a think-aloud activity. In the think-aloud portion, I prompted participants to find information related to sexual health questions using only Google Search. Participants walked through their search processes for specific questions including chosen search terms and evaluation of search results.

Contribution: Findings suggest that participants relied on previous knowledge including understandings of Google Search to guide their search strategies and interpretation of search results. In this unique health and LGBTQ+ context, participant conceptions of search engines have implications for health decision-making and identity formation. Understanding the incorporation of search engines into the sexual health information seeking of LGBTQ+ youth might also better prepare educators and providers to connect young people with relevant and credible resources in accessible formats.

Patient and Public Involvement in Clinical Research with the Visually Impaired *Kayo Takashima, Kyoto University; Jusaku Minari, Kyoto University*

The concepts of patient and public involvement (PPI) and patient engagement have been attending to create a patient-centred knowledge based on dialogue and engagement in medical research practice. This presentation explores the point of considering these activities for appropriate information provision and the informed consent process, together with scientists and potential research participants. Specifically, we use the PPI example of the regenerative medicine field, in which eye disease is one of the frontier areas. In line with this analysis, we identified two key concepts of the informed consent process for the visually impaired. These concepts are 1) 'concept summary with key information' of the US common rule and 2) the Convention on the "reasonable accommodation" policies that came out of the Rights of Persons with Disabilities. These offers the essential points to provide a clear understanding of informed consent without visual information. This presentation will suggest three elements to consider for PPI, including various stakeholder engagements, using the example of enabling the user to clearly understand the research information via audio recording material, without relying on visual information. The first consideration involves the selection of professional stakeholders while recruiting patient and public members. The second is the appropriate process of stakeholders' involvement. The third element is the coordination of each stakeholder's opinion. Overall, these three elements include the concept of science communication.

Session Organizer:

Stephen Mollidrem, The University of Texas Medical Branch

Chair:

Stephen Mollidrem, The University of Texas Medical Branch

Discussant:

Victoria Neumann, Lancaster University

424. Uses, strategies and knowledge production in mobility contexts - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Participants:

The 'Becas Chile' program and the scientific mobility in the production and circulation of knowledge: motivations and strategies of doctoral students. *Claudio Broitman Rojas, Universidad Andrés Bello; Patricia Rivero, Universidad de Córdoba*

We analyze the effects of international mobility on the modes of production and circulation of knowledge. Our case study focuses on the 'Becas Chile' scholarship program holder's motivations and strategies. This program is the most important scientific funding initiative of the Chilean scientific-technological system. Its goals are to increase the research capacities and deepen the research internationalization. The implementation of this system is also linked to the approach of "brain circulation", which points out that international mobility increases the scientific and technological human capital of the fellows and that this will result in greater development in the origin country. Hence, the policy of training abroad is oriented towards a commitment to mandatory return and thus to avoid a "brain drain". For scholarship holders, the compulsory return has important effects on the production of knowledge. Firstly, they have deliberate reasons for choosing certain research topics as the knowledge acquired is expected to be applied in the origin country, while it can also be a strategy for optimal professional reintegration. Secondly, as a consequence of a scarce follow-up at the moment of reinsertion, scholarship holders generate their own strategies to face the precarious labor conditions in the academic field, which entails few possibilities of producing and transferring knowledge. All of this together strains the very notion of social appropriation of knowledge to which the Becas Chile program would aspire in principle.

Resisting the standardization of the "globalized" social sciences through the exposition of their unquestioned formatting *Sarah Cordonnier*

Over the last decades, the huge raise of international mobility of people (students as well as researchers), and the wider availability of scientific publications, led neither to the acknowledgement of a greater diversity of knowledge forms in social sciences nor to the "true intellectual universalism" Bourdieu called for in his well-known article "the social conditions of the international circulation of ideas" (1999). Indeed, the "internationalized" social sciences have known various kinds of standardization, partly resulting from the spreading of neoliberal "excellence" policies in academia and from the increasing scarcity of tenured positions, but also from their translation in formatting routines. This contribution will clarify and address these routines through the observation of the apparently mere neutral expectations formulated by "international" conferences or journals. Those "devices" (Foucault) are generally unnoticed and unquestioned despite their deep effects upon the knowledge production and evaluation and, thus, upon the researchers submitted to them, especially the young professionals and/or those in "peripheral" countries. Therefore, it is crucial to expose the ways in which these frames contribute, discreetly but fundamentally, to the homogenization of formats, topics, postures; to the invisibility of alternative ways of thinking, theorizing, investigating, being a professional researcher; while too often sanitizing, decontextualizing, depoliticizing, homogenizing the "internationally recognized" knowledge. Paying closer attention to these apparent trivialities of the academic life should thus give us leverage to advocate for fairer, more creative ways to produce and to share knowledge in

mobility, within and from the social sciences.

Theoretical-conceptual reconstruction of the paradigms of "brain drain" and "brain gain" of brains: scenarios and current degree of relevance in the Latin American region
Patricia Bárbara Flores, Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación-Argentina

The objective is to present a theoretical-conceptual historical reconstruction of scientific mobility from the middle of the 20th century to the present, based on studies in the field of science and technology and society - CTS (Loray, 2017; De La Vega and Vargas, 2017 ; Luchilo, 2011; Vessuri, 2009; Albormoz et.al. 2002). Through this journey, we seek to reflect on the current relevance of the "brain drain" and "brain gain" approaches - and the classical and structuralist positions that surround them. For this, it is reviewed how the postulates and terminologies of both currents were forged, within the framework of scientific-technological and socio-economic conjunctures of the countries involved in the flow of researchers, with a focus on the situation of the Latin American region, and making allusion to the Argentine case. From a center-periphery perspective regarding the north-south economic and scientific-technological development asymmetries (Kreimer, 2011, 2006; Hurtado, 2010), it deliberates on the opportunities for south-south collaboration, within the framework of a scientific nomadism , but aimed at reaffirming ties with geographic partners in similar conditions and / or with research lines of mutual interest (Didou Apetit and others 2009, 2014). Likewise, It is analyzed the importance of the proliferation of case studies by disciplinary fields with mixed methodological approaches (Rivero et.al 2021; Luchilo et.al., 2019; Moreno, 2017), as a contribution to the improvement of planning and management scientific public. Finally, it is presented the transnational approach.

Alternative Ways of Knowledge Production in an Age of Mobility and Precariousness/AWKPAMP Eylem Camuroglu
Cig, University of Bayreuth

Since 2016, the forced/political mobility of intellectuals in Turkey has been discussed within the context of "brain drain" in mainstream discussions. Erdoğan's new presidential regime first targeted the scientists, journalists, artists, politicians etc. who produce critical knowledge and art. With the law decrees enacted during the state of emergency, Erdoğan regime dispossessed the intellectuals and deprived them both of their professions and of their basic rights and freedoms. As a consequence, many of the dispossessed intellectuals had to leave the country in order to continue to produce critical knowledge and art. The discussion about the "exiled intellectuals" from Turkey mostly focused on the brain drain. But these discussions failed to notice the fact that the critical knowledge production of these exiled intellectuals still continues and affects the intellectual and political sphere of Turkey as well as transnational spaces. Moreover, they have been creating solidarity networks on transnational level that carry the possibility to create alternative ways and institutions of knowledge production in our neoliberal, precarious world. As a vivid example, I will discuss the "Academics for Peace" case, the academics who signed a peace petition in 2016 and faced with very different sanctions afterwards, with a special emphasis on their solidarity networks and the potential of a critical knowledge production despite their vulnerability and precariousness in Turkey as well as neoliberal Western academia. Via this example, I will critically analyze "brain drain" discussions with respect to accumulation by dispossession, precarity and neoliberal state.

Describing Social Sciences' Knowledge Through Public Places And Private Mobilities : Story Telling Of Le Lieu-Dit And Le Manifesten
Antoine Lalonde, Université Paris Sorbonne

I would like to share the results of an ongoing PhD research which aims at describing and thinking social sciences' knowledge. My approach consists in discussing critical works on

popularization of science (Jurdant, 2009 [1973]), criticism of modern science (Latour, 1992 ; Stengers, 1993) and spatial studies of science (Livingstone, 2003). My analysis is based on observations and interviews conducted in French radical leftwing gathering and meeting places and venues, such as libraries and cafés. Indeed, the creation of such public places are often secretly related to life trajectories of people confronted to forced mobility, exile and precarity (Le Marec and du Plessis, 2020). In this way, one of the main goals of my work is to understand the role that places situated on the fringes of academics networks might have in the circulation and construction of social sciences' knowledge. It also leads me to notice possible links between the creation and upkeep of these places, and the trajectories and mobility of their creators and residents. However this inquiry has also shown knowledge could not be apprehended without it being considering as truly situated standpoints (Haraway, 1988). Henceforth, social sciences' knowledge can only be understood and described through the muddled stories (Haraway, 2016) of these places and of those who build and inhabit them. Therefore my communication will be focused on two stories. That of an Iranian political refugee who created a café in Paris in 2004 (Le Lieu-Dit). And that of an anarchist doctor in political science involved in an alternative space in Marseille (Manifesten).

Session Organizer:

Patricia Rivero, Universidad de Córdoba

Chair:

Claudio Broitman Rojas, Universidad Andrés Bello

Discussant:

Jöelle Le Marec, Université Paris Sorbonne

425. Viral Relationalities II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

These are unprecedented times, or so we are told through COVID-19 communications articulated by global health institutions and national governments. Such exceptionalism foregrounds the significance of the current crisis – its bodily and economic impacts, the global and local inequities that have materialized and the myriad meanings it has created. Yet this exceptionalism, in practices and discourses, also gives rise to hierarchies of knowledge production. Ontologies and epistemologies advanced by global and national health responses construe the virus as a discrete, measurable entity. Such dominant framing might connect COVID-19 with other epidemics, as for instance HIV, but disarticulates the viral from local marginalized knowledges and modes of worlding. Consequently, borders are erected - geopolitically, between bodies and knowledge generating disciplines, temporalities, and across socio-economic differences - in the name of exceptionalism. What queer, Indigenous, and decolonial knowledges, histories, embodied effects and meanings can be highlighted if we understand that COVID-19 and other epidemics are exceptional through the particular relations they put in place or displace? This panel doesn't dismiss COVID-19's local and global significance, but instead invites contributors to inhabit virality's exceptionalism in relational terms: querying science's entanglements with politics; reconceiving intimacies and viral transmission; positing other temporalities and post-COVID futurity narratives. Papers in this Session together with its companion Session, Viral Relationalities I consider: - viruses' entanglements with pre-existing states of perpetual crisis - practices of survival and imaginings of futurities as lived by ethnic, racial, sexual and gender minorities - other means of embodying post-colonial/settler colonial realities in the viral present

Participants:

Communal Ties in a Pandemic: On a Queer Coalition for Health Equity
Yidong Wang, University of Wisconsin-Madison

The Covid-19 pandemic recontextualizes community in the disruption of interpersonal relationships. On the one hand, scientific models and protocols urge people to isolate and minimize contact with others. On the other hand, the failure of public health and other social support systems denies the most

vulnerable access to essential resources and necessitates care via community networks. The perspective of how communities are affected by structural disfranchisement is further obscured in the scientific discourse of the pandemic, as the authority of science is already politicized on the partisan front. LGBTQ people, as one of the minoritized groups in the history of medical science and administration, continue the work to sustain community care networks and archive alternative knowledge about the coronavirus. In this paper, I will examine a community-based project I participate in and present a relationship-oriented account of pandemic countermeasures that goes beyond numbers and statistic models. In 2020, as part of the local queer advocacy network, I convened a coalition of LGBTQ organizations based in Madison, Wisconsin. One goal of the coalition was to amplify the community support that was already building to mitigate the pandemic's impacts. We launched a campaign named "Queer We Are, Together We Heal" and paid particular attention to identifying how communal ties were situated within structural factors leading to health disparities. By reviewing this project, I propose a queer reimagining of viral relationality that destabilizes the linear understanding of epidemiological interventions and reconciles the individual and the community in the design of public health institutions.

Exploring Digitally Aided Humanitarian Intervention Of Support Service Professionals In Combating The Shadow Pandemic In India *Sreyasi Chatterjee, Prasanta Chandra Mahalanobis Mahavidyalaya*

Through a provocative question—"Are Stay-at-home orders enough to combat the COVID-19 pandemic?" this study intends to deconstruct normative conceptions of COVID-19 communication as communicated by expert knowledge systems promoted by government and health agencies in India. Significant focus on the physiological impact of COVID-19 have been used to justify stay-at-home orders. Forced nationwide lockdown in India had confined vulnerable genders at home, forcing them to cohabit with their abusers. Limitations on movement had further isolated gender-violence survivors from community participation and disrupted safe channels of communication. Increased instances of gender violence may have earned the moniker "Shadow Pandemic", yet it is neither a new phenomenon nor was it unexpected. All knowledge production with regard to the pandemic have ignored its entanglement with structured gender-based injustices. Through group interviews and face-to-face interviews of fifty professionals who have provided support services to cope with the 'shadow pandemic' in India, this study explores how digital technology has been used to provide humanitarian intervention and to challenge hegemonic knowledge creation systems that have dominated COVID-19 communication. This study argues that COVID-19 protocols have established the idea of home as a safe space, ignoring instances of domestic violence. The support service professionals used digital technologies in their innovative strategies to rehabilitate survivors, reconstruct channels of safe communication, enabling survivors to rebuild their everyday lives in the 'new normal'. The study contributes to understanding the role of digital technology supported interventions that aim to integrate all survivors in the knowledge production systems surrounding the pandemic.

Epidemic Uncertainties and the construction of risk in emerging infectious disease (EID) epidemics. The case of Ghana. *John Kojo Aggrey, Louisiana State University; Wesley Shrum, Louisiana State University*

Uncertainty is a characteristic feature of emerging infectious disease (EID) epidemics. Although scientists develop new knowledge in the midst of an epidemic to curb some uncertainties, people are still faced with the uncertainty of being exposed and infected by the causative pathogen and suffering the harm of infection. Risk, a measure of these uncertainties, and a

form of knowledge required in an epidemic context is deemed necessary in reducing the possibility of infection. This paper conceptualizes and interrogates risk as an epistemic construct in epidemics to understand the social processes by which it is constructed and identify the constitutive elements which influence its construction. Using qualitative interviews and comparing rural and urban populations in Ghana, I argue that the construction of risk as an epistemic construct is influenced by a combination of disease/networked knowledge and contextual factors triggered by the disease risk characteristics. These contextual factors shape the disease risk characteristics which then amplifies or attenuates the perceived risks of people and the health behavior exhibited thereof.

Hundreds, thousands, and counting: Death tolls as rhetoric during HIV/AIDS and COVID-19 *Claire McDonald, The Information School, University of Washington*

As a novel disease is identified, particularly one which is easily transmissible and potentially fatal, medical and political authorities must make decisions about how to share their specialized knowledges with the general public regarding the nature of the threat that they will potentially face; however, this process of translating expert knowledge about the nature of the novel disease and its victims is often problematized by the very authorities seeking to inform the public and mitigate the threat. In comparing the New York Times' coverage of two ongoing public health crises—the HIV/AIDS pandemic and the COVID-19 pandemic—I intend to examine the circumstances in which a disease's death toll is used as a rhetorical device to support claims about each disease as a threat to readers' individual and collective health, as well as the gradual process by which these diseases' death tolls are normalized. HIV/AIDS' initial prevalence in gay men and intravenous drug users catalyzed the development of narratives about the disease's victims and the disease itself, in academic publications as well as in the New York Times; the staggering death toll of HIV/AIDS is initially presented as an inevitable conclusion to the victims' lifestyles and gradually normalized, no longer being perceived as newsworthy despite the rapidly rising death toll. The sheer speed at which the death toll of COVID-19 rises, without easily being mapped onto a few marginalized communities, has resulted in news coverage which presents information about the disease as a threat while memorializing its victims.

Session Organizers:

Rory D Crath, Smith College

Annette-Carina van der Zaag, Birkbeck, University of London

Paul Boyce, University of Sussex

426. Nonhuman Phenomenology and Technoscientific Intersubjectivity - 4: Subjective Attunements

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Participants:

Talking Tails: (Inter)subjectivity and collaboration in Dutch pig farming *Else Vogel, University of Amsterdam - AISSR*

This paper approaches animal subjectivity not as a question of capturing the 'perspective' of the animal, but explores it as a pragmatic problem of those who work with animals on a daily basis. In empirical philosophical mode, I trace how situations 'offer both humans and animals different opportunities to accomplish subjectivities.' (Despret, 2008: 123) The situations I discuss pertain to scientists' engagements with tail biting, an urgent animal welfare problem in pig farming in the Netherlands. Although illegal under EU law, farmers routinely cut tails to prevent pigs from biting each other when stressed. Animal welfare scientists argue, however, that the state of pigs' tails is revealing of a broad range of welfare issues and thereby a valuable 'iceberg indicator'. Like beak trimming in poultry and dehorning in cattle, pig tail docking is meant to adapt animals'

bodies and behavior to current industrial housing standards. Exploring under what conditions docking could become obsolete in today's livestock industry, by contrast, forces farmers, scientists, and others involved in farming to address animals as sentient, social and vulnerable beings. To explore how tail biting could be prevented, scientists diligently trace pigs' responses to small changes in housing systems and toys to overcome boredom. Their studies, I suggest, come down to posing a difficult question to the pig: Are you content? I will discuss how pigs' capacity to respond is configured in the research practices I studied; what this capacity asks of farmers, scientists, and others involved; and what it makes of animal subjectivity.

Dwelling with Animals: Space, Species, and Subjectivity in Habitecture *Richard Fadok, MIT*

As climate change, biodiversity loss, and other anthropogenic disruptions impose unprecedented degrees and kinds of proximity, encounter, and conflict with nonhuman animals, a growing cadre of ecological architects are mining ethological information about animal phenomenology (how animals perceive, construct, and navigate space) in order to learn how to better accommodate them in human-oriented worlds: for instance, within bat towers, but also within artificial reefs for oysters and highway overpasses for wolves, deer, and other critters. By measuring and replicating how animals construct their own habitats, or niches, practitioners of "habitecture," also known as "animal-inclusive architecture," aim to decentrer humanity as the arbiter of spatial "norms and forms"—a dogma of Western architectural praxis from the ancient theorist Vitruvius, through modernism's Le Corbusier, and up to current talk of "human scales." This paper analyzes the discourse of habitecture to diagnose these mutations in design's subject. Clearly, when architects design not just for animals, but through their phenomenologies, they fashion new criteria of taste, and new relations to the animals with whom they share ground, too. This paper offers the concept of "dwelling with" to capture the aesthetic, ethical, and political quandaries that surface as architects negotiate the pragmatics of public and private co-existence. Conceptualizing dwelling as an inter-subjective and trans-specific relationship between animals and the habitects accommodating them illumines relations of space, species, and subjectivity, i.e., how architectural divisions based on experience, orientation, and other phenomenological categories are lines and planes of domination and exclusion but also of resistance and revolution.

Nonhuman Witnessing: Invisual Perception and Algorithmic Relations *Michael Richardson, University of New South Wales*

Consider an edge-computing algorithm onboard a militarised drone, doing real-time analysis of sensor data to elevate certain relations between elements to a plane of action that can potentially lead to violence. Or take the image classifiers taught by the research agency Forensic Architecture using synthetic media to recognize tear gas canisters in social media feeds. Or even the vast machine of planetary computation that assembles diverse data into climate change statistics with a political valence. This paper argues that these and many other algorithms undertake a form of nonhuman witnessing that is premised on the production of relations through forms of invisual perception (Mackenzie and Munster 2019) in which images no longer take their meaning from things in the world but rather in relation to the elements and edges of other images. Attending to the invisibility of algorithmic systems foregrounds the production of relations, both within the algorithmic systems and in their extractive, instrumental and analytic relation to worldly phenomena. In this paper, I combined STS methods of situated and media-specific analysis with witnessing theory to argue even without a witnessing 'subject' in the unitary, humanist sense, witnessing occurs within and through algorithmic systems. Through necessarily brief examinations of invisual perception

and algorithmic relations in drone war, activist art and climate surveillance systems, the paper reveals both the differences and commonalities of nonhuman witnessing across distinct sites and technics. In doing so, it contributes to STS scholarship on algorithmic systems by developing an ethico-political conception of their knowledge-making processes.

How to Work with Fungi: Interspecific Collaboration and Sensorial Engagements *Juliette Salme, FNRS - University of Liege*

Relying on the tools of biotechnology and sometimes referred to as "biofabrication", an emerging field is gathering people who are experimenting with living (micro)organisms as a way of designing more sustainable alternatives and cleaner production in the area of manufacturing. Many do-it-yourself biologists, designers, and amateurs as well as professional scientists are particularly interested in working with mycelium, the vegetative part of fungi, as it can be harnessed to produce a wide range of biodegradable materials (e.g., packaging, construction, and textile). Working with microorganisms requires engaging with invisible entities; and engaging with those entities requires finding ways to develop a multisensorial understanding of those organisms and their ways, one that unfolds on a day-to-day interspecific relationship relying on direct, sensory engagement that sometimes exceeds ocularocentrism as well as rigid scientific protocols. Drawing on an ongoing ethnographic research conducted in Western Europe, this paper addresses how those practices of growing materials in collaboration with microbial nonhumans invite us to reflect on how humans may get to know such organisms that are so alien to them. To know how to work with fungi one needs to know how a particular fungal specimen works—that is, what is it, what does it need to thrive, how to understand and handle its sometimes unpredictable reactions, and how to actually feel and engage with that nonhuman.

Session Organizer:

Richard Fadok, MIT

Chair:

Claire Isabel Webb, University of Southern California

Discussant:

Eva Hayward, University of Arizona

427. (Re)materialising Cancer: Bodies, Cells and Environments - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

Bioscientific approaches to identifying, classifying and diagnosing cancer have long enrolled practices that engage with the materiality of tumour tissues and cells, such as cytology and histology. In the contemporary era, scientific techniques detect and act upon cancer outwith tumour tissue itself. For example, pre-cells, inflammatory cells, immune system T cells and microbes are becoming understood to play a role in cancer. Molecular pathology has also allowed for exploration of the makeup of cancerous tissues as inscribed within genetic code, and can 'diagnose' predispositions to cancer. Such techniques, along with designations of cells as 'pre-cancerous', add a temporal dimension to the materiality of cancer. These approaches locate cancer within structures and organisms beyond the tangibility of tumour tissue, and demonstrate that various elements of bodies and their environments continuously interact to constitute the disease. Contemporary scientific work thus generates a picture of cancer as more than malignant, fleshy tumours, with the disease materialising in genes, healthy cells, and wider (bodily) environments. This refigures the material constitution of cancer, blurs clinical categorisations of tissues and cells as malignant or benign, and prompts us to think about cancer in ways that unsettle widespread 'fixed' sociocultural understandings of the disease. In this session we will discuss configurations of cancer that disrupt understandings of the disease as manifested in a malignant, fleshy, tumour. We ask 'what constitutes cancer?' and address the implications of these diverse configurations for scientific and clinical practice, embodied experiences, patient subjectivities, and sociocultural depictions of cancer.

Participants:

The Figure of the Cancer (Micro)Celebrity: Constituting Cancer Cultures *Lisa Ashmore, Lancaster University, UK; Brigit McWade, Lancaster Medical School*

This paper examines the construction and configuration of cancer through the figure of the cancer micro-celebrity, exploring how social media influencers enact particular framings or figurations of the ideal cancer patient/consumer. The influence of celebrity on everyday lives is classed, gendered, racialised and taps into neo-liberal demands to produce oneself as a subject of 'value'. Within cancer celebrity cultures, the specific enactments of cancer, via stories shared, are embedded in a culture of vitality and optimism, linked to monetization and biopolitical processes. Legitimate patienthood is increasingly intertwined with being able to transgress illness, obscuring/sublimating other lived experiences of cancer that are less optimistic, less coherent, less normative, and less media-savvy. Even with the detailed descriptions of very challenging treatment effects, there is a performativity that exudes whiteness, heterosexuality, choice, autonomy, consumerism and aesthetic perfection. Through a figurative analysis of the cancer micro-celebrity, we trace the enactment of cancer experiences as constituted in and through specific social, cultural and economic contexts, paying attention to how multi-layered structural inequalities and their intersections configure and interact in these sociocultural depictions of cancer experience. Finally, we critically reflect on the implications of such enactments for the embodied and situated experiences of people living with or caring for someone with cancer, cancer-clinicians or those yet to be diagnosed with cancer.

Is cancer made of objects? Material culture as a constitutive part of women's malignancies *Susana Noronha, Centre for Social Studies - University of Coimbra*

Bringing together objects and materialities that take form and gain relevance in artistic projects representing female experiences of cancer, this presentation proposes alternative concepts of material culture and malignant diseases. It rejects a separation or differentiation between material and intangible dimensions of illness, understanding objects of material culture as constitutive parts of cancer, that is, of the ideas, sensations, and emotions that shape the experience of being diseased, undergoing treatment. Medical, domestic and personal objects, of collective or individual use, including disposable materialities, clothing, furniture, and machines, such as - waiting room chairs, syringes, imaging technologies and linear accelerators, hospital beds and gowns, surgical instruments, drains, prostheses, implants, IV bags and poles, infusion pumps, wigs and scarves - compose a list of realities that are embedded in our experiences during diagnosis, treatment, reconstruction, remission, recurrence, metastization and death. Objects are thus understood as modular components of our cancer experiences, inseparable from our bodies, from what they feel, think and do during illness. To understand the effects, uses and meanings of these objects, the working field of this investigation included the images and written explanations of one hundred artistic projects made by or with women with cancer stories. Looking at the many organs and malignancies represented in these artistic projects, but also to women's representations of oncology's material culture, this investigation points to the outline of another ontology, a "third half of things" where people, tumours, experiences, objects and different forms of knowledge are parts of an indivisible sum.

Radiotherapy and the Ambivalence of a Pharmakon *Mette Kragh-Furbo; Lisa Ashmore, Lancaster University, UK; Vicky Singleton, Lancaster University; Hilary Stewart, Lancaster University*

Radiotherapy kills cancer cells, with either the intention of cure or slowing progression; yet alongside its therapeutic effects, radiotherapy also causes short and/or long-term effects. Effects

of treatment include, amongst others, sore skin, tiredness, feeling sick, and diarrhoea as well as changes in sexual health and wellbeing, fertility problems, lymphoedema and psychosocial issues. Drawing on the pharmakon as a conceptual tool (Derrida 1981), we examine the ways in which radiotherapy holds a paradoxical pharmakon status: it is both a remedy at the same time as it is toxic. We draw on preliminary findings from a project on women's experiences of radiotherapy treatment for gynae cancer, discussing the complex and often ambivalent effects of radiotherapy, how it treats but also reconfigures bodies and identities. We analyse the manifestations as well as politics of this ambivalence, exploring whether and how ambivalence may be unwisely obscured or underplayed. We conclude by asking whether ambivalence may offer a productive space for reflection and for generating new ways of supporting patients who undergo radiotherapy treatment for cancer.

Invisible Tumors: Seeing, Knowing and Proving Visceral Cancers in Haiti *Rebecca R Henderson, University of Florida*

In Haiti, patients often arrive at the country's few oncology departments only when they have large external tumors. While there are no national cancer statistics for Haiti, breast cancer is by far the most common type of cancer treated, in contrast to other settings in which lung, colorectal, prostate, and stomach cancers are common. Due to a lack of cancer knowledge and diagnostic resources, cancers that are not externally visible are often never diagnosed- creating a hypothetical group of cancer patients who are thought to exist, but who never formally have cancer. At the same time, when such cases do present to oncology centers, pathological confirmation of a cancer diagnosis is often impossible, imaging is expensive and imperfect, and tumor markers are unavailable. In cases where the tumor cannot be physically seen, measured or touched, therefore, oncologists often left without vital information needed to treat or track the disease. Using 20 months of fieldwork at the two largest cancer treatment programs in Haiti, a tracking of patients and their tumors through pathology labs, radiology centers, blood banks, and other sites of care, and interviews with clinicians and patients, I seek to understand the process of knowing a cancer which is never seen, touched, or proven. What is cancer when it never becomes more distinct than a murky shape seen on an unclear ultrasound? What does it mean to be treated for, live with, or die from a cancer that is hypothetical or invisible? How are decisions made in the absence of materiality?

Session Organizers:

Emily Ross, The University of Sheffield
Julia Swallow, University of Edinburgh

Chair:

Maria Temmes, Tampere University

Discussant:

Julia Swallow, University of Edinburgh

428. Networking Rurality Part 2

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Rural communities' information infrastructures are slow to build out and prone to breakdown, potentially hampering their economic opportunities. Technology companies are addressing these challenges by developing new networking capacities for farms and rural communities, often with state-based support and incentives. Rural connectivity is promised to transform the provision of data to, and collection of data from, rural and remote areas, and thereby to transform rural life. But will such transformation be positive and seamless? What approaches might STS scholars bring to bear to critically analyze the digitalization of rural life? For instance, what pre-existing mechanisms of social cohesion in farm and fishing communities might be disrupted by the push to digitalize? Will networking technologies which enable economic mobility also place pressures on rural practices to conform to urban imaginations? Will rural information connectivity

projects follow state-supported infrastructure projects like rail, telegraph and telephone, which led to the consolidation of agricultural and communications industries? How does high-bandwidth information communication access and its effects vary based on geopolitical contexts and relative wealth of rural communities? This panel seeks to explore the intersection of the rural (and ideas of the rural) with novel ICT technologies like internet infrastructure provision. It examines how the possibilities and problematics of networked rurality are co-constructed by technology developers, rural residents, and policy makers, and how they are shaped by or diverge from long histories of rural expropriation. The panel will also speculate on how emergent technologies could be channeled into alternative trajectories.

Participants:

Asset Maps and the Digitization of Rural Opportunity Jean Hardy, Michigan State University

An expanding high-tech economy paired with an affordability crisis in America's biggest tech hubs has drawn attention to opportunities for economic growth in small cities and rural regions. This increased attention has spurred economic developers and rural municipalities to rethink the role of outsiders in local economies and come up with new tactics for attracting investment in a distributed virtual world. Drawing from ethnographic research in the rural Midwestern United States, I explore one of these tactics: the digital asset map. In this paper, I describe how local and nationwide mapping initiatives have pushed for the digitization of rural community-based asset data, from water and sewer infrastructure to breweries and mountain biking trails. I show that while the increased demand for digital asset data is marketed as efforts to repopulate and revitalize rural communities in decline, the resulting mapping initiatives actually draw attention to and reify the stark divides between the rural haves and the rural have-nots.

Resource Wars Against Rural Communities and Their Networks Christopher Csikszentmihalyi, Cornell University

Researching rural communities facing petrochemical extraction in the United States, our team witnessed massive informational (and other) infrastructures being built and renewed. The private and proprietary infrastructure for extraction is built at the expense of other infrastructures: farming disrupted, roads degraded, water fouled, and civil society infrastructures co-opted and captured. The extractive information infrastructure was as unidirectional as the 4' pipelines pulling gas from the ground: satellite communication trucks at drilling sites and 3g modems on wellheads relayed information back to Houston and Calgary, depicting the changing streams of chemicals being fractured into groundwater, but the locals who farmed with and drank the water remained ignorant of the composition because its secrecy was protected by law, and industry ran active disinformation campaigns. Assaying the damage to livelihoods, bodies, and environment, I was left wondering if this was a form of low-level resource war: a war by growing cities on valuable but easily-conquered rural areas, whose occupants were left describing their communities as "national sacrifice zones." Can these damaging exchanges be reformulated? And are rural-specific information infrastructures necessary, ones that may help to resist co-option and capture? I'll briefly describe a series of attempts to design possible forms of rural information systems with these goals in mind, including the ExtrACT project and RootIO.

The Preservation of Embodied Masculinity in Tech-Altered Workplaces Jenna Burrell, School of Information, UC Berkeley

Tech sector work is often thought to represent a shift from an old regime that favors physical strength and capability to a new one favoring disembodied human intelligence. By contrast, the occupational values of traditional rural industries in the Western United States (including, logging, commercial fishing, and cattle ranching) persist in centering the laboring body. Rural work of this sort is celebrated and even mythologized as physical,

perilous, embodied, and done in the outdoors. So what happens when the work worlds of high tech make inroads into rural places? How do communities respond when the livestock auction becomes Internet-connected and a Facebook data center becomes the newest employer in town? Drawing from ethnographic work in Central Oregon and the Northern California coast, this paper explores how rural workers reconcile occupational values when disparate work worlds intersect in rural sites. A recent trend reclaims digital work from the realm of weightless 'ephemerality,' situating it instead in the material world, a world of brutal, embodied physicality. For example, in an interview for *Outside* magazine, Ken Patchett, director of the Facebook data center in rural Prineville, Oregon insisted, "The Internet is not a fake thing...it's a very, very real thing made with hammers and concrete. And nails. And blood and sweat and tears and people" (Streep 2017). This study accounts for how tech work is made suitable and meaningful in rural sites through its connection to embodied masculine identity.

Welcome to the Digital Village: Networking Geographies of Agrarian Change Hilary Oliva Faxon, UC Berkeley

Almost five billion people—two-thirds the global population—now go online. The internet has changed how we work, learn, govern, and fall in love. Yet new work in STS and critical data studies has only begun to grapple with the patterns and significance of internet connection for rural people and places, particularly in the Global South. In this paper, I bring together agrarian studies and digital geography to situate emergent online practices within longer trajectories of agrarian change in Myanmar, where the recent arrival of mobile internet is embedded in sweeping rural and political transformations. Drawing on three years of ethnographic research, I show how farmers, migrants and grassroots activists of two ethnic groups incorporate Facebook into daily efforts to secure livelihoods, support communities, and mobilize in struggles over land. This analysis yields two key insights: first, agrarian questions increasingly play out in online spaces; second, digital geographies extend far beyond the city and are shaped by rural relations. To understand internet in the global countryside, I advance the notion of the digital village, a networked geography in which interlinked on- and offline practices both sustain and transform rural life.

Technologies of Land Dispossession: Digital Agriculture and Legibility Jen Liu, Cornell University

To address increasing environmental challenges around climate change, computational technologies are increasingly being developed and implemented to address environmental sustainability goals. For example, digital agriculture is framed as a set of technologies that can address challenges around resource management in the agricultural industry. However, these technologies may also perpetuate legacies of land dispossession and occupation that may run counter to these efforts towards sustainability. In this presentation, I develop the concept of legibility in the design and development of digital agriculture systems to understand how these legacies are retained. In this context, legibility is defined as bringing situations and environments under control through processes of simplification, such as quantification and subsequent optimization. I draw from fieldwork on the implementation of digital agricultural systems and a historical analysis on scientific agricultural policies in the United States to demonstrate how technologies have been geared to modernize farming at the expense of rural Black and other marginalized communities in the United States. In reading this fieldwork together with the historical case, I address the question: what is made legible to whom? Subsequently, what becomes illegible? As more data-driven systems are used to address challenges around climate change, I argue that we need to extend the ways we understand how these systems impact the governance of labor, labor, and resources in rural communities.

Session Organizers:

Jen Liu, Cornell University
Phoebe Sengers, Cornell University
Kelly Bronson, Department Of Sociology And Anthropology,
University Of Ottawa
Matt Comi, University of Kansas

Discussant:

Kelly Bronson, Department Of Sociology And Anthropology,
University Of Ottawa

429. East Asia Science and Technology Society Editorial Board Meeting

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

East Asia Science and Technology Society Editorial Board Meeting

Participant:

East Asia Science and Technology Society Editorial Board
Meeting *Hsin-Hsing Chen*, *Shih-Hsin University Graduate
Institute for Social Transformation Studies*

East Asia Science and Technology Society Editorial Board
Meeting

Session Organizer:

Hsin-Hsing Chen, *Shih-Hsin University Graduate Institute for
Social Transformation Studies*

430. Diverse, inclusive and caring engineering relations II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

This panel invites papers that studies efforts to make engineering and engineering education more inclusive, diverse and caring. Engineers engage in design, development, testing, modifying, installing, inspecting, monitoring and maintaining a wide variety of infrastructures, systems and products. They make recommendations, evaluate, supervise, consult and some of them teach future engineers in colleges and universities. Engineers potentially play a pivotal role in designing for a more diverse, inclusive and caring society in the future. We call for papers that analyze attempts to make engineering more diverse and/or caring. This could be efforts to redefine engineering practices or engineering education. Broadly speaking, this include studies of initiatives to transform engineering practices, organizations and cultures to make them more caring, ethical, diverse and inclusive and thus helping to develop a more sustainable society that protect people, cultures, communities and environments. It also invites papers about how to make engineering more welcome and inclusive for groups and minorities. It also welcomes paper discussing the need to change the understanding of engineering and what engineers are for, what changes that are called for, and what this may mean for engineering identities. Further, we welcome critical reflections on research practices, methodologies, language and perceptions in engineering studies, including the performativity of engineering studies and reflections on what represent good relations for engineering as well as reflections on how the field may configure engineers and engineering work and education.

Participants:

Careful Engineering - Why Engineering Education Needs

Feminist STS *Sahra Dornick*, *Technical University Berlin*

Processes of technology development and technology design are deeply gendered. Therefore, a fundamental change in the professional culture is needed in order to eliminate discrimination and marginalisation due to gender and other social inequality structures. Even though the implementation of gender and diversity issues within engineering education is still in the beginning, social and environmental responsibility of engineers are coming into focus due to fast technological and ecological changes of our world. Diversity and inclusivity are becoming increasingly important for engineering sciences since technical artifacts are more and more required to be planned with regard to the resources needed, applicability, climate justice and social justice. The paper presents a study of the one-semester

compulsive module Blue Engineering at Technical University Berlin (TU Berlin), which is designed to raise social and environmental awareness and responsibility of engineering students. Homepage research, ethnographic observation and a qualitative analysis of 17 learning journals written by students of the module are used to explore (1) how the gender and diversity unit was perceived by students and (2) if being taught social and environmental responsibility helped engineering students to develop a caring attitude towards marginalised humans and more-than-humans. Results show that engineering students aim to learn about social and environmental awareness and responsibility and that further adjustments with respect to Feminist STS would make it easier for them to approach the entanglement of gender, diversity and engineering.

Engineers, Robots, and Work: Imagining an Inclusive and Just Future? *Yunus Dogan Telliel*, *Worcester Polytechnic Institute*

Current public debates around robots and other autonomous systems succumb to either techno-pessimism and techno-optimism. While proponents of the first believe that the adoption of these systems will eventually move large populations out of workforce and rob them of their ability to support themselves and their sense of identity and moral worth, proponents of the latter consider the very same trend as the liberation of humans from the necessity of work. Both promote a view of future that is technologically-determined. Yet, some North American engineers still operate with the assumption that in the foreseeable future workplace will remain human-centric, and human control, input, and guidance will shape the success of human-robot collaboration. This assumption is also reflected in changing priorities of some funding programs supporting research in robotics. Although engineers play a crucial role in the design, development, and delivery of work-related robotic technologies, the 'future of work' debate tends to overlook their ethical commitments and future imaginations. Drawing on an ongoing anthropological research, this paper discusses how engineers articulate the future implications of their practice for themselves, their colleagues, and the broader public. In line with the conference theme, my discussion will focus on two questions: 1) in what ways do engineers move beyond a narrowly-framed calculus of jobs created or made obsolete, and think about the quality, security, meaning of work in new technology ecosystems?, and 2) to what extent do they align their research and design practices with an inclusive and equitable vision of the future workplace?

"Why we teach": reasons for choosing engineering education as a career *Atsushi Akeru*, *Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute*; *Sarah Appelhans*, *Bucknell University*; *Alan Chevillie*, *Bucknell University*; *Thomas De Pree*, *University of New Mexico Health Sciences Center*; *Soheil Fatehiboroujeni*, *Purdue University*; *Melissa Shuey*, *Bucknell University*

Many assume amidst the hectic pace of academe and the prestige accorded to research in higher education that most engineering educators choose to follow in their advisors' footsteps because of the promise and excitement of contributing to the world of engineering knowledge. However, in having completed 270 interviews of engineering educators and administrators across a broad cross section of US engineering schools and colleges and other academic institutions, it's clear that engineers who choose a career in academe do so for a variety of reasons. In this talk, we employ the method of narrative analysis to analyze how educators account for their own experiences, their past, and the reasons they give for choosing an academic career. While there are those who do in fact seek the rewards and reputation that come with scholarship, there are others who are equally passionate about teaching and their connections with their student. Individual biographies, and their personal retelling in fact reveals an intricate web of meaning spanning different

institutional settings and embedded values that become woven into the reasons for their choice of career trajectory. The story is partly US-centric, in that different careers and motivations map onto the diversity of the institutional settings in which engineering education is offered in the US. However, it also harkens to the observation made by Ken Alder (1997) in reference to French engineering education that differences arise as much through our decisions about what to hide. Through our data, we help bring different stories about engineering educators into greater balance.

Moving Beyond Promises: Constructive Technology Assessment as Engineering Design *Brandiff Caron, Concordia University, Montreal, Canada*

This paper will critically examine the role and intended function of tech for good declarations and seek to situate the, too often well-deserved, charge of “ethics washing” levelled against many of the most prominent instantiations of these declarations. “Ethics washing” is the charge that rather than representing a good faith promise to adhere to a set of ethical standards, one is instead engaged in mere “ethical theater” or “window dressing” when declaring adherence to a code of ethical conduct, often attributed to a desire to avoid external regulation that could potentially actually constrain or limit the conduct of those who design technology. Those engaged in ethics washing are not committing themselves to the kinds of changes that are required to address the ethical crises that gave cause for such declarations to become so prevalent in the first place. By appeal to the literature and praxis of constructive technology assessment and the scholarship growing out of the “Design Justice” movement, this paper will show how many of these charges are indeed well-deserved and how those who seek to engage in good faith efforts to guide the ethical design of emerging technologies can commit themselves to a more practical, action-guiding set of principles that move beyond the declaration of good intentions to a real commitment to more inclusive design practices that center the voices of those who are directly impacted by the outcomes of the design process. In doing so, the ethical considerations that tech for good declarations aspire to emerge as constitutive components of the design process itself.

Transforming Computer Engineering Pedagogy Through Anti-Racist, Trauma-informed Frameworks *Yumi Rosa Aguilar, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo; Emily Flores, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Victoria Siaumau, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo; Lauren Cooper, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo; Jane L Lehr, California Polytechnic State University; Lynne Slivovsky, California Polytechnic State University - San Luis Obispo*

Women-identified people of color - particularly Black, Indigenous, and Latinx women - are particularly underrepresented in Cal Poly’s Computer Engineering Program (CPE). CPE’s distribution of male and female computer engineering students reflects national averages: 89.5% and 10.5%, respectively. However, ratios without context mask the bigger problem: student lack of persistence within the major. Disqualification rates for students from racially minoritized groups are 234% greater than for white students. Likewise, women-identified students are 60% more likely than male students to be dismissed from CPE. CPE is grounded in dualisms commonly used to create hierarchies in engineering thought and practice (rational-emotional, male-female, concrete-abstract, etc.). This context produces a situation where students from minoritized groups are pushed to hide or discard multiple aspects of their identities to present themselves as (stereo)typical computer engineers. With the binary choice of “in” or “out,” many of these students leave the field. Our goal is to engage with students to formally characterize the current state of the program’s culture concerning endorsement or rejection of

historical binaries in engineering, constraining Cal Poly CPE students by normative social constructions of gender, race, and socioeconomic class connected to the field’s disciplinary identity and approaches to professional formation. To do this, we developed a trauma-informed, anti-racist framework protocol to collect data about student experiences through surveys and interviews over a 5 year period. We hypothesize the data yielded from this protocol will support the CPE program’s effort to create a culture of diversity and belongingness.

Session Organizers:

Vivian Anette Lagesen, NTNU
Atsushi Akera, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute
Jessica M. Smith, Colorado School of Mines
Cyrus Mody, Maastricht University

Chair:

Vivian Anette Lagesen, NTNU

431. Publication Politics II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

This double panel brings together multidisciplinary approaches to investigating the relationships between publication practices and science in diverse national and transnational settings. It puts into conversation research that uses qualitative and quantitative methods and analyzes to investigate the development of the field of Innovation Systems studies, the trajectory of STS social science in Brazil, that articulation of Sustainable Development Goals in Brazilian publications, and the ways citizen science publications represent the motivation for “participation.” The panel takes up the question of how scientific publications represent the status of statistical “significance” in Austria, Germany, and Switzerland, as well as critically investigates the role of peer review in STS journals themselves, and the status of the “non-human” in design journals, and even the role of google searchers and hence algorithms in generating results. In so doing, the panel turns a critical eye to both the study of publication in the sciences as well as within STS itself.

Participants:

Motivation for Participation in Citizen Science: A Bibliometric Analysis *Hazal Baytok, Université Paris-Sud/Paris Saclay*

This paper presents the findings of the bibliometric coupling analysis carried out to explore the research on the motivations for participation in citizen science. Different disciplines that constitute a foundation for the participation motivations in citizen science will be examined. This way, it is possible to understand which knowledge domains have shaped the current literature on motivations to participate in citizen science. Understanding the origins of participation dynamics in citizen science plays an important role in analyzing the existing mechanisms for knowledge generation and enables to incentivize participation by developing new methods. The analysis is based on all the articles retrieved from Web of Science, which focus on motivation of participants. A total of 885 articles were retrieved, and a clustering analysis carried out based on common citation patterns between articles to identify main knowledge domains.

“Peer review has always been a fucking nightmare”. Review and editorial practices in STS journals *Wolfgang Kaltenbrunner; Kean Birch, York University; Maria Amuchastegui, York University, Canada*

In popular as well as scientific discourse, peer review is often thought of as a purely epistemic operation where intellectual gate-keepers (itself a simplistic term) pass judgement on the interest of a submission and its ability to innovate conceptually, empirically, or in terms of providing an original critical outlook. Especially in peer review literature produced by scientists, there is moreover a longstanding concern with identifying ‘bias’, conceptualized as a deviation of publishability judgements from certain intellectual norms. This pristine notion of peer review as an application of stable quality criteria has only recently been

problematized by STS scholars and historians, who have inter alia pointed to the constitutive role of negotiation dynamics among referees and editors as well as economic constraints on review labor. We extend this line of thinking through a detailed study of review and editorial practices in our own field of STS. Drawing on 75 interviews with editors, editorial board members, and referees of various STS journals, we specifically focus on how the work of these actors is always situated and as such configured by the following factors: access to commercial publishing infrastructure & labor (or lack thereof); strains on the review economy due to increased submissions; almost universal concern with metrics like the journal impact factor; a reflexive concern of journals with positioning themselves in a growing landscape of publishing outlets; and increasingly prominent questions of representation and exclusion in review and editorial work.

Re:search-A transdisciplinary methodological framework for search *Renée Ridgway, Copenhagen Business School*

Google Search has now become a ‘media a priori’ (Peters 2015), enacting habitual behaviours such as ‘ubiquitous googling’ that simultaneously organises (users) (Ridgway 2021), facilitated by the social constellation of ‘surveillance capitalism’ (Zuboff 2015, 2019). In this presentation I elucidate how I carried out ‘truth games’ (Foucault 1984) with algorithms by designing an ‘experiment in living’ (Marres 2012) as a ‘critical technical practice’ (Agre 1997). I queried Google and Tor with the same set of chosen keywords (input) on two computers: a ‘hacker approved’ PC using Tor (The Onion Router) that obfuscated my IP address, the other a completely personalised Mac, where Google tracked me based on my IP address. Applying modern memory tools (hupomnēmata) with my ‘technology of the self’ (Foucault 1982), I conducted qualitative ‘interviews’ with algorithms—and captured this human/algorithmic interaction by collecting data on myself. The result, ‘Re:search-Terms of Art’, is a series of ‘data visualisation as transcription’ that compares my personalised and anonymised search results through coded outputs—URLs. Hinging on ‘locative data’ (Google) or ‘off the map’ (Tor), these ‘critical cartographies’ as practices of representation seek to intervene and give shape to the world by making invisible infrastructures and their effects more tangible. Although situated at the interstices of Organisation Studies, Media Theory and Artistic Research, this interdisciplinary methodological framework has recourse to STS scholarship and it is not without limitations. As a ‘deskilled’ (re)researcher (Galloway 2014) I draw on ‘The Cybernetic Hypothesis’ (Galloway 2014) to contextualise my small data set, which contrasts the fetishisation of tools and correlations produced with ‘big data’.

Sociology of Science in Brazil: themes, approaches and institutions by scientific papers published between 2010 and 2018 *Marília Luz David, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS/Brasil); Lorena Fleury, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS); Adriano Premebida, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS); Jalcione Almeida, Federal University of Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS)*

The aim of this paper is to examine the Brazilian scholarship in Sociology of Science drawing on a similar research previously done in Anthropology (ROHDEN; MONTEIRO, 2020). To do so we analyze articles published between 2010 and 2018 in 16 Brazilian scientific journals classified as A1 (the highest in rank by Brazilian research funding agency CAPES). Initially, we ran keyword queries in the Scielo database (a national academic virtual public library) which turned in 602 abstracts. Subsequently, article selection was based on two criteria: i) a theoretical perspective and literature associated with STS was found, and/or ii) technoscientific practices were considered as empirical objects. Our final set consisted of 147 articles which

were fully read. We seek to analyze the consolidation of Sociology of Science as a fully formed field in Brazil, pointing out to its most current themes and disciplinary approaches, and situating such scholarship in the country’s broader discipline. In our results we highlight the prevalence of empirical research (94 articles = 63% total), top 10 institutions (per article frequency) and most frequent themes, empirical objects, and concepts in Brazilian scholarship. We also analyze qualitatively the top 4 most frequent themes: namely, “health”, “science and technology policies”, “gender” and “innovation”. We investigate their trending topics and their interfaces with broader Brazilian sociological scholarship.

Where are non-human animals in the design discourse?

Deconstructing the Animal “Myth” *Elif Gökaltay*

The Covid-19 pandemic is a reason to reconsider the manner in which how we treat and sustain our relationships with the non-human animal world. Could parallelism be pinpointed between the non-human animal’s status in the world and the design discourse? This paper addresses the human-centeredness of the field of design while searching for the non-human animal in its discourse by scanning four major design journals for the keywords: “animal” and “non-human”. The paper includes a review that covers the journals: “Design Issues”, “Design Studies”, “Design Journal”, “International Journal of Design”. The results of the searches made with the terms “non-human” and “animal” are then categorized in regards to what they actually refer to and for what purpose they are mentioned. By the categories derived, the non-human animal’s presence and position are argued by borrowing the concept of “myth” by Roland Barthes. Finally, it is discussed that by seeking new ways of relating to non-human animals, new opportunities could be explored that will enrich both the lives of non-human and human animals, as well as the field of design. This paper will offer a perspective regarding an area of intersection between the field of design and multispecies studies.

Session Organizer:

Wolfgang Kaltenbrunner

432. Sense ecologies: new technologies and strategies of environmental surveillance - III

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Drones and mounted cameras monitoring wildfire ignitions. Satellites detecting areas of deforestation and reforestation or the transport of agents through ocean currents. Weather stations tracking humidity and rainfall surrounding monocrops. Video cameras poised to capture evidence of rare or threatened species, while bodies and wearable medical devices register the presence and passage of industrial pollutants. Sensors and modes of sensing are part of infrastructures that monitor and mobilize environments, constituting atmospheres of data, knowledge production, and world-making (Gabrys 2019). These ‘sense ecologies’ are differentially charged with promise when imagined and enacted (Spackman and Burlingame 2018), sometimes with expectations that they might deliver a world without surprises (Masco 2014). In practice, the promise of recent and new environmental sensing technologies are highly ambivalent. Their proliferation has been crucial to projects that hold powerful state and non-state actors to account, while (often concurrently) being enlisted as vectors for state securitization, targeted discrimination, corporatization and neoliberal intrusion (Mansfield 2008). Whatever their use, new sensing technologies are powerful, often compromised (Liboiron 2017), and are increasingly widespread means for imagining, constituting and intervening in environments. This open panel seeks contributions that examine new techno-imaginaries of environmental surveillance, including (but not limited to) analyses of sense ecologies and their ‘good’ or ‘bad’ relations, sites and practices of sensing, the promises of sensing technologies, ecologies of attuned sensing, distributed sensing networks, and the privatisation of sense ecologies. References: Gabrys, Jennifer. 2019. Sensors and Sensing Practices: Reworking Experience across Entities, Environments, and Technologies. *Science, Technology & Human Values*

44 (5):723-736. Liboiron, Max. 2017. Compromised agency: The case of BabyLegs. *Engaging Science, Technology, and Society*, 3, 499-527
Mansfield, Becky, ed. 2008. *Privatization: property and the remaking of nature-society relations*. Oxford: Blackwell.
Masco, Joseph. 2014. *The theater of operations: National security affect from the Cold War to the War on Terror*. Durham, NC: Duke University Press.
Spackman, Christy, and Burlingame, Gary. A. 2018. Sensory politics: the tug-of-war between potability and palatability in municipal water production. *Social Studies of Science*, 48(3): 350-371.

Participants:

Sensing Land Dispossession: Aerial photography and surveying in early 20th century oil and gas exploration *Sabrina Peric, University of Calgary*

While sensors are often presented as a new technopolitical intervention on environments, they are part of a longer genealogy of sensory transformation by human-nonhuman networks. This paper examines one such sensory transformation that took place in the early 20th century in Canada's North: the adoption of aerial surveying and photography by oil and gas corporations. Previously, corporate geologists described oil and gas exploration as a largely opportunistic and improvisatory process based on building good relationships with northern communities. Highly reliant on Indigenous guides, corporate geologists required immense on-the-land experience and environmental knowledge to navigate the rivers, muskeg and mountains in permafrosted lands. The fortuitous assemblage of geologists, bush pilots, planes, cameras and lenses, however, fundamentally changed the sensory practices of oil and gas exploration. Not only did aerial surveying and photography systematize oil and gas exploration, but also rendered unnecessary both the expertise of corporate geologists, as well as their abilities to build and sustain social relations in the North. New aerial photographic sensory systems simultaneously removed Indigenous communities from the process of exploration, thereby contributing significantly to the land dispossession central to settler colonial processes. For this paper, I draw heavily on the Imperial Oil Archives, housed in the Glenbow Western Research Centre at the University of Calgary, thereby arguing not only that new sensory technologies contributed to dispossession, but also that sensory technologies structure environmental data into repositories now most easily accessible to settler populations, and not the people who actually live on the sensed land.

Surveilling Species: The Politics of Turning Facial Recognition Technologies onto Animals *Madisson Whitman, Columbia University; Geneva M.L Smith, Dartmouth College*

Developments over the last several years in facial recognition technologies (FRT) have enrolled animals into surveillance environments. From industrial cattle farming in Ireland to grizzly bears in conservation contexts in Katmai National Park, Alaska, FRT has become more accurate at identifying animal faces and predicting animal behavior, owing in part to the fact that these technologies are not trained on humans. In contrast, FRT for human faces has been widely criticized for its failure to recognize darker skin tones and its cisheteronormative gaze (Buolamwini and Gebru 2018; Keyes 2018). These failures speak to tensions around embedded surveillance technologies aimed at making bodies visible in particular ways and the environments created to support certain kinds of sensing (Browne 2015). But who and what is made (in)visible when the subjects of FRT are animals? And how should these technological developments be treated and understood differently from those being developed for humans? Multispecies ethnography has made a point to de-center the human (Ogden et al. 2013), but, we ask instead what it means when it is the technologists who de-center the human. We engage these literatures in an effort to re-center the human that is implied in the development of FRT for animals. In this presentation we explore the sensing ecologies that draw together humans, animals, data, and environments, probing at implications for

knowing, recognizing, and predicting these environments.

The techno-imaginaries of Atmotube: Visualizing VOCs beyond technoableism *Sophia Jaworski, University of Toronto*

This paper explores the techno-imaginaries activated when a personal air monitor creates data about total volatile organic compounds (TVOC), a proxy air quality measure for the cumulative levels of hundreds of different molecules which volatilize, or turn into gas, at room temperature. VOC levels are exponentially higher in indoor atmospheres, yet, they receive much less attention than outdoor air pollution. Human-made petrochemical fumes and vapours emanate from consumer products such as cigarette smoke, air fresheners, and cleaners. Highly reactive, they oxidize and attach to particulate matter, create combinatory clouds of secondary reactions. A series of images I produced using an "Atmotube" personal air monitor as part of the UC Irvine Centre for Collaborative Ethnography Visualizing Toxic Places project led by Dr. Kim Fortun, reveal large variations in exposures structured by low paid labour and rental housing environments that may be missed in lab-based scientific studies. On the one hand, live exposure level graphs paired with fieldwork offer new ways to understand the complexity of atmospheres with the potential for long-term health effects beyond normative conceptions of able-bodiedness. However, sensors can reinforce metrics and logics of surveillance that feed into what Ashley Shew (2020) has termed 'technoableism' if the levels detected dismiss sensitivities to chemicals at levels below what is termed 'safe' by existing thresholds. Thus, mobilized to complicate existing definitions of toxicity, VOC monitors have the potential to guide anti-ableist forms of "collaborative air quality infrastructure" in indoor spaces (Houston, Gabrys and Pritchard 2019).

Elemental Activism: Blue Governmentality on Poaching Seas *Adam Fish, University of New South Wales*

The elements--atmosphere, water, and their stormy convergence--afford three mediations. As media for the physics of waves, the elements mediate communication through electronic excitation and molecular vibrations. As material for the physics of motion, the elements suspend sensing hardware and living bodies. As a medium for the physics of chemistry, the elements support life by carrying oxygen and other life-giving sustenances. These three elemental mediations are made explicit in political action with unpersoned aerial vehicles or drones, as well as ships, helicopters, and other technologies. Informed by archaeologist André Leroi-Gourhan, this presentation interprets drones as 'liberations' of human vision, mobility, and force into exterior environments. This process is revealed through an empirical investigation into the Sea Shepherd Conservation Society, an international non-profit ocean conservation organization innovative in their use of oceanic and atmospheric technologies in agitating for the intrinsic worth of biodiversity. Following Leroi-Gourhan, atmospheric and elemental technologies link Sea Shepherd's deep ecological 'interior milieu' with an 'exterior milieu' of elemental turbulence and ocean exploitation. The drone's 'technical tendencies,' or socio-technical potentials, manifest within Sea Shepherd as situational awareness for mission planning, documentation of illegal activity, and spectacular imaging for political campaigns. Paradoxical to their deep ecological principles, the use of such technologies performs an elementally-specific type of powerful control between ecopower and geonotpower, what I call blue governmentality. In short, this talk makes an empirical argument about how the elements mediate political governance through physics and technologies.

The Sesame, the Drought, and the Index: Sensing Agrarian Environments Through Weather Insurance *Caroline Schuster, Australian National University*

Much of the critical debate about IBAI – index-based agricultural

insurance – in social studies of finance has focused on new configurations of risk. By purchasing a weather derivative that triggers under certain agroclimatological conditions, poor, rural households are re-imagined as pivotal financial agents engaged in risk management (Johnson, 2013; Taylor, 2016). This paper suggests that while the absorption of vulnerable agrarian communities into speculative finance surely merits critical engagement, focusing exclusively on the end-users of IBAI ignores the grid upon which the insurance product is engineered. Sensing technologies – including satellite rainfall data, telecommunications infrastructures, meteorological data from local weather stations, and app-based forecasting data – generate this grid, which monitors and mobilises the environments of niche cereals like sesame and chia. Based on a year of ethnographic fieldwork on commercial farms in Paraguay, this paper offers an anthropological interrogation of how the weather index is created as a ‘sense ecology,’ and how its atmospheres of data are mobilised for financial gain. Crucially, an anthropological perspective on weather sensors and the environments that they monitor reveals alternatively generative grids with their own sense ecologies: namely, genealogical grids of kinship that suffer and that respond to the ‘bad’ relations of financial sense ecologies. Johnson L (2013) Index insurance and the articulation of risk-bearing subjects. *Environment and Planning A* 45(11): 2663–2681. Taylor M (2016) Risky ventures: Financial inclusion, risk management and the uncertain rise of index-based insurance. In: *Risking Capitalism*. Emerald.

Session Organizers:

Timothy Neale, Deakin University

Alex Zahara, Department of Geography, Memorial University

Chair:

Will Smith, Deakin University

433. Toxic Entanglements: acting on slow, invisible, and emerging realities - IV: Feminist/Queer Approach to Toxic

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

Allergic to the Twentieth Century: Multiple Chemical Sensitivity and Biomedicine’s Earthly Imaginaries *Cole Adams, Duke University*

Sufferers of Multiple Chemical Sensitivity (MCS), a so-called “contested illness,” describe asthenia, asthma, and migraines that follow exposure to industrial chemicals such as pesticides and petroleum products. Spurred by public pressure in the early 1990s, the U.S. Department of Health and Human Services assembled an MCS taskforce that produced an ambivalent report. At this same moment the ongoing HIV/AIDS crisis and “epidemic of signification” was raging and queer theory coalesced in the American academy as a kind of defensive response to a profusion of paranoid discourses attendant to the permeability of the human body and the national body. Todd Haynes’ film *Safe* (1995) notably brings these material-semiotic entanglements to the fore. This paper draws on medical research, historiography, and queer STS to situate MCS within a broader history of biocapital that extends at least as far back as George Miller Beard’s study *American Nervousness* (1881), in which he proposes a pathological vulnerability of the human organism coincident with developments in capitalist industry and technoscience. Why does a porous, sensitive, and passive bodily imago return to haunt the popular consciousness at the close of the twentieth century? Contested illnesses like MCS feel out the episteme’s body imaginary and offer psychosomatic knowledge of possibilities for the body’s materialization. Through the confluence of the discursive fields of MCS and HIV/AIDS, we see how institutional biomedical imaginaries solidify a national body that projects threatening differences outward and ultimately facilitates shifts in the distribution of economic and corporeal

precarity that fuel the capitalist world-system.

Emerging hormonal ecologies in the aftermath of the crisis of “the pill” in France *Mariana Rios Sandoval, CERMES3*

Young women in France are increasingly turning away from ‘the pill’ for contraception, signalling the crisis of a contraceptive method that has been the bedrock of French family planning for more than fifty years, the access to which is still collectively imagined as an emblematic victory of the second wave feminist movement, and which is still by far the most prescribed contraceptive nationwide. In this presentation I will share insights from two years of research on emergent contraceptive practices—spearheaded by young feminists—that escape from the dominant, pill-centred contraceptive model, and which unsettle normative social, medical, bodily, and environmental relations. This research reveals that the pill is called into question in its materiality and relationality. First for being deeply engrained in a model that regulates women’s fertility, reproduction and sexuality within the boundaries of the gynaeological profession, heteronormative relationships, and republican universalism. And second, for the asymmetrical and cumulative chemical exposures resulting from this model, which affect in the first place the bodies of those daily swallowing pills for extended periods of time, but that also transform bodies of water and potentially disrupt those of other non-humans during the pill’s afterlife. Through practices such as auto-gynaecology groups, botanic walks to identify plants of gynaeological use in city parks, or genital self-exploration workshops new hormonal ecologies emerge, which expand far beyond the gynaeologist’s office and the individual body, and where hormones, hormone-like chemicals and toxicants are harder to tell apart.

Sex Hormone Ecologies as Speculative Ecologies and Ecologies of Speculations *Lenka Veselá, Brno University of Technology, Faculty of Fine Arts*

In my contribution, I propose the notion of “sex hormone ecologies” as a mode of relating to the world through imaginaries of molecules with the ability to affect sex, sexuality and reproduction (among many other things) of living beings. There is an uncertainty about how much endocrine disrupting chemicals (EDCs) interfering with biosynthesis, metabolism and functions of physiologically produced sex hormones reach and affect humans and wildlife. Taking this uncertainty as a starting point for my inquiry, I ask: how are these gaps in knowledge filled by speculative narratives and to what effects? Most scientists warn that despite the lack of direct, irrefutable evidence, EDCs are truly harmful, with their effects on what is considered “healthy” sexual and reproductive development being of particular concern. Meanwhile, industrial manufacturers and distributors mobilize the uncertainty to refuse responsibility for possible “side effects” of their products. In contrast, some artists and activists speculate narratives not grounded in normative, static understandings of bodies and sexualities and imagine hormonal landscapes as sites of indeterminacy and queer becoming (rather than sites of pollution) and conceive of them through the notion of care (rather than of “concern”). I interrogate these different narratives and circuits of knowledge in order to determine possible entry points into the problematics of sex hormones and hormone-mimicking substances — the different ways of knowing these chemicals as well as different ways of going about not knowing enough about them.

Temporalities of Toxicity: Navigating Emerging Scientific and Embodied Knowledge about Diethylstilbestrol (DES) over a Lifetime *Jacquelyne Luce, Mount Holyoke College*

What does it mean to be “DES-exposed”? How does this identity – confirmed or constructed through clinical assessment or triangulation – shape one’s relationship to chemical toxicity? This paper is part of a larger project which explores how circulating knowledge about diethylstilbestrol (DES), a synthetic hormone, continues to shape scientific and everyday understandings of

gender/sex/sexuality. DES exposure was first associated with a rare vaginal cancer, then more commonly with reproductive and genital tract differences and fertility and pregnancy complications. In the 1990s, DES was recognized as the prototypical "endocrine disrupting chemical", significantly expanding awareness of its potential effects and the lens through which these are viewed. In this paper, we take a close look at emerging knowledge, clinical guidelines, and advice about hormonal toxicity and the cumulative risk of exposure to exogenous estrogens over the past 50 years. We bring disparate strands of feminist STS engagement with the slow and diffuse toxicity of DES together with the narratives of DES-exposed individuals now in their 60s and 70s. How have DES-exposed individuals navigated emerging scientific and embodied knowledge about DES over time? What are the temporalities of toxicity? How do interviewees reconcile their understanding of the harm inflicted on them through exposure in utero, with their intentional use of hormones for various purposes? Drawing on 24 interviews with trans, cis, straight, and queer individuals who identify as DES-exposed, we trace interviewees' stories of knowledge, risk and desire, highlighting discursive and embodied entanglements of chemical toxicity with chemical potentiality.

Visualizing Occupational Harm: A Methodological Reflection on Counter-Mapping with Nail Technicians *Reena Shadaan*

The nail salon is a site of occupational harm. Nail technicians report a multitude of health issues and concerns rooted in their exposure to workplace toxicants, unergonomic design, and the conditions of precarious work. In the Greater Toronto Area, nail technicians tend to be newcomer and immigrant-settler women of Chinese, Vietnamese, and Korean descent. Their work conditions reflect the racialized-gendered division of labour in which precarious, low-wage, and undervalued labour, including service and care work, is offloaded to racialized and newcomer women. Yet the nail salon remains an underacknowledged site of occupational/toxic violence. As a workplace, the nail salon is a site of slow violence where harm is incremental and, as a result, "out of site" (Nixon, 2011). However, Davies (2019) asks: "Out of site to whom?" – a reflection on the erasure of community- and worker-based situated and embodied knowledges. "Visualizing Occupational Harm: A Methodological Reflection on Counter-Mapping with Nail Technicians" reflects on these themes via a discussion of occupational health mapping – a worker-led methodological tool that visualizes corporeal manifestations of workplace harm. From August 2019 – February 2020, a series of occupational health mapping workshops were held with 37 Toronto-based nail technicians. The worker-participants produced visualizations of the corporeal implications of their exposure to workplace hazards, including toxicants. As a method, occupational health mapping contests top-down approaches that construct workers' bodies as research "subjects," such as in biomonitoring. The method is rooted in and demonstrates that workers are the experts of their bodies and work environments.

Toxic White in the Philippine's Service Sector *Anita Hardon; Mai Taqueban, University of the Philippines*

In this paper we explore the interpersonal dynamics and institutional policies that perpetuate colorism in the service sector in the Philippines, attending to the highly material work undertaken by service sector workers in order to "do" the white skin that their employers expect of them. Gender shapes these practices, as we saw with the young men in the Philippines who are competing with women for service sector jobs – many of them embrace skin whiteners just as their female peers do. Having light skin takes on a specific value in interactions in the service sector, where lighter skin can attract clients and thus have economic value. We show this form of institutional colorism contributes to the precariousness of youth people who are not born with light skin. But the discriminatory work policies, and the selling and marketing of skin-whitening products by personal

care companies are not just harmful because they perpetuate a culture cycle (Markus and Conner 2013) that privileges having white skin: they are also harmful because many skin-whitening products contain toxic chemicals, which can disfigure those who use them. Through multimedia exhibits and mini-documentary we created experimental spaces in which to resist hegemonic notions that equate white skin with intelligence, beauty, and wealth; in the process, values attached to skin colors are re-imagined. But the impact of these cultural expressions is limited in countries with retail markets that are saturated with skin-whitening creams, scrubs, and soaps, and media landscapes that amplify the idea that fair skin is better.

Session Organizer:

Anita Hardon

SATURDAY, OCTOBER, 9

434. Assisted reproductive technology and Third Party Reproduction in East Asia: Japan and Taiwan

6:00 to 7:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Assisted reproductive technology (ART) allows the use of third party sperm and eggs, and reproductive tourism is caused by economic disparity, price disparity, medical level disparity, and differences in legal systems. Within the same East Asian region, Taiwan has a legal system for reproductive technologies involving third parties, while Japan does not have a legal system for reproductive technologies involving third parties. This difference in legal systems has encouraged reproductive tourism, and the number of people traveling from Japan to Taiwan to receive sperm and egg donation seems to be increasing every year. On the other hand, in Japan, private sperm donation between individuals is becoming more and more apparent. While Taiwan is tolerant of fetal reduction surgery, Japan is intolerant and has avoided it by limiting the number of transplants. This panel will examine the differences in the governance of technologies surrounding reproduction and the resulting micro-experiences of individuals in Japan and Taiwan.

Participants:

How govern reproductive technologies-An analysis of the current debate in Japan *Minori Kokado, Kobe Pharmaceutical University, Japan*

With advances and global expansion of assisted reproductive technologies (ART), there is an urgent need to determine how to regulate it. How do we protect the right of donor conception children to know origins, how do we protect donors, what are the requirements for ART users, and what principles are these based on? This paper examines the recent debate on the ART regulation in Japan, working from the assumption that laws regulating ART reflect the values and beliefs of the society in which they are enacted. In Japan, ART is widespread, however there was no law until the end of 2020, and opinions of the Japanese Society of Obstetrics and Gynecology (JSOG) served as guidelines. According to these guidelines, married couples can carry out ART using their own gametes or artificial insemination with donated sperm. Since egg donation and surrogacy are difficult to carry out in Japan, couples who wish to undergo them are engaged in reproductive tourism. Under these circumstances, legislation was needed, and the ART Act was passed after a short debate in parliaments at the end of 2020. However, the new law has been criticized for its lack of mention of children's rights and other issues. What is needed for a better ART law for ART users, children, and donors? In this paper, we will examine this question by comparing the laws of France, where established Bioethics laws in the mid-1990s and continues to discuss ways to improve them.

Family members as gamete donors in Japan *Yukari Semba,*

Ochanomizu University

In Japan, donor anonymity has been maintained to protect donors' privacy since the first child conceived by donated sperm was born in 1949. However, there is a worldwide trend to eliminate gamete donor anonymity in order to secure the wellbeing of donor offspring, and in the future Japanese donor offspring will likely be able to identify their donor using consumer DNA testing—indeed, some are reported to have already done so in other countries. As a result, many men who would otherwise consider anonymous sperm donation are anxious that they might be identified in the future. The number of sperm donors is decreasing drastically in Japan and there is currently a serious shortage. Under these circumstances, it is difficult for infertile couples to find a sperm donor, and some couples use gametes donated by family members. In 2001, the Japanese government set up the Committee on Assisted Reproductive Technology to consider drafting a new ART bill. The committee discussed gamete donation within family circles and concluded that it should be prohibited because it would complicate family relationships and cause parent–child relations to become unstable. In addition, it was thought that a family member identified as a potential donor might be subject to intense pressure from other family members. There is no law yet in Japan regarding gamete donation within the family. In this presentation, I will discuss the pros and cons of intra-family gamete donation in Japan.

How to choose a country for egg donation: Egg donation between Japan and Taiwan *Chiaki Shirai, Shizuoka University*

In the present era, Japan and Taiwan are linked by eggs, not by international marriage or intercountry child adoption. Choosing an egg from someone other than herself is an unprecedented experience for a Japanese woman, and this choice involves the country. In recent years, the number of Japanese clients traveling to Taiwan for egg donation has increased, and the geopolitics of reproductive tourism in Asia has changed. Why do Japanese clients choose, or sometimes do not choose, Taiwan? We examine the reality of egg donation for the parties based on data from ongoing interviews with the involved parties. Positive remarks may be generally summarized as the rationality and convenience of the clinics being close, being cheap, providing a clear schedule, and being able to serve clients quickly, and the positive remarks also included the resemblance of the child and parent by way of them both being Asian. Negative remarks were related to the client's inability to choose a donor, the absence of information on the child's origin, and the need for the child to be homogeneously Japanese. Positive and negative evaluations of egg donation in Taiwan suggest that women who have difficulty in pregnancy and childbirth with their own ova may be in conflict with cultural norms, such as parent-child homogeneity and strategic rationality to maximize the likelihood of having a child. This situation of egg donating and implanting is a conditional, rational choice that varies from person to person.

Reproductive Providers or Patients? Egg Donors' Experiences and Status of Fertility Treatments in Taiwan *Yuling Huang, National Cheng Kung University*

This paper explores egg donors' experiences of healthcare in assisted fertility practices in Taiwan. As assisted reproduction technologies, including cryopreservation techniques, have advanced in the past two decades, such progress also redefines what it means to be a patient in the fertility clinic. The demand of egg donation (ED) increases and fertility clinics are recruiting more young women as donors. Nevertheless, we know little about how these donors experience the third-party reproduction, especially care quality. Adopting the concepts "participatory/imposed enrollment" and drawing insights from 25 interviews with egg donors and clinic staff, fertility clinics' websites and advertising materials, and the Internet forums, I

portrait the egg donor's ambiguous patient status and healthcare from four aspects: recruitment, informed consent, relationship, and risk prevention. The recruiting work by the clinic staff is efficient, yet sometimes constraining the donor's questions and concerns. Donors are not aware of the justiciability of Informed consent forms, in which the "penalty" of incomplete retrieval process and short number of eggs is highlighted. Few consistent one-on-one relationship with the clinic staff and less doctor-physician active engagement provided throughout the ED process. The planned protocol for effective egg retrieval sometimes ignores the donor's unique medical and personal needs. This paper discusses three factors that cause the status ambiguity of egg donors: fixed yet high monetary compensation, altruistic framing of ED, and constant concerns about recipient couples. Further research on bioethical mechanisms of third-party reproduction is needed.

Ethical Boundary Work and the Fetal Reduction Politics in Japan and Taiwan *Chia-Ling Wu, National Taiwan University; Chiaki Shirai, Shizuoka University; Hsieh Hsinyi, National Taiwan University*

This paper compares the trajectories of fetal reduction, one of the most controversial reproductive technologies, in Japan and Taiwan. Data includes archives, interviews of stakeholders, and participant observation of clinical practices. In Japan, the medical society examined the first case of fetal reduction, caused by the traditional infertility treatment, within the arena of abortion. The procedure and indication of fetal reduction was scrutinized to decide whether it violated Eugenics Protection Law. Comparatively, in Taiwan, the first fetal reduction case was presented as a medical breakthrough to solve the problem of multiple pregnancy caused by multiple embryos transferred during IVF. Rather than being treated as life-killing procedure, it was portrayed by the leading IVF experts as life-saving technology, and part of IVF system. The ethical boundary work was settled differently in Japan and Taiwan. In Japan, the dispute was ended when the medical societies agreed that fetal reduction fits in with the legal definition of abortion. Its controversy led to the strong efforts in prevention of multiple pregnancy, including building one of the strictest guidelines in the world to limit the number of embryos transferred during IVF. In Taiwan, only feminist health activists briefly challenged the prevalent use of fetal reduction during the stipulation of Assisted Reproduction Law in early 2000s. The action did not continue so fetal reduction remains to be a routine practice in IVF. We conclude that the ethical boundary work of fetal reduction needs to be contextualized in larger historical, social, and political contexts.

Session Organizer:

Chiaki Shirai, Shizuoka University

435. Corona Truth Wars: Testing and Contesting Knowledge in a Hyper-Mobile Pandemic - III

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

The SARS-CoV-2 pandemic created a global crisis challenging humankind to develop as quickly as possible reliable knowledge about the virus and its devastating effects on our bodies and societies in order to minimize such harms. This situation of great uncertainty and enormous stakes incited a historically unique international knowledge producing effort by institutionalized scientists and research groups. While debate and disagreement exists within these scientific communities, more controversial are the various competing "outside" forms and sources of information on the virus and its mitigation strategies. Some are clear disinformation campaigns or far-fetched conspiracy theories, others are legitimate challenges to the temporary status quo. In the hyper-mobile context of knowledge production during an evolving pandemic, it is often hard to tell the difference. Questions such as 'what information is reliable?', 'which experts should we follow?', and 'what (epistemic) authorities are to trust?', take center stage in public debates. Prevalent clear-cut distinctions between "real" knowledge controversies and "fake" disruptions of scientific

progress obscure the fact that the global quest for truthful knowledge about the virus is entangled with various (geo)political dynamics, government policy pressures, media reporting, platform moderation and public understandings of it all. STS scholars are perfectly equipped with concepts, theories and methods to help understand these complex dynamics involving uncertainty, changing insights, and (covert) manipulation. In this panel we invite scholars working on such “corona truth wars”: we welcome both empirical and theoretical studies on the cultures, politics and technologies of today’s corona knowledge contestations.

Participants:

Censorship of covid-19 heterodoxy *Brian Martin, University Of Wollongong*

The covid-19 pandemic has stimulated a huge amount of research about treatments, vaccines and control measures. Although understanding about these matters has been changing as new information is acquired, many governments, media organisations and technology companies have taken steps to silence the expression of views deviating from the current official line. This has included failure to report on heterodox views, changes in search algorithms, abrupt removal of websites, and reprisals against dissidents. Individuals and groups raising non-orthodox views have been subject to derogatory labelling, for example being called conspiracy theorists. As well, there has been an imbalance in research, with neglect of careful studies of treatments using non-patentable substances and relatively little study of the harmful effects of control measures. The result has been a one-sided body of knowledge and a one-sided information environment. This suggests the influence of governments and large corporations over the production and distribution of knowledge, and fits with the concept of “undone science,” in which research unwelcome to powerful interests is not carried out. Interviews were carried out with scientists and doctors critical of covid-19 orthodoxy. Their perceptions and experiences show the processes by which dissent has been marginalised, including by covering up dissident views, devaluation of dissidents, rationalisations for censorship, ineffective appeal procedures and intimidation. The censorship of heterodox views raises questions of power and knowledge, in particular whether worthwhile ideas are being excluded from public discussion in the push to ensure that publics adhere to official recommendations.

Corona Conflicts in Germany. Old and New Constellations of Discourses, Practices and Groups *Ehler Voss, University of Siegen*

The proclamation of the SARS-CoV-2 pandemic has created a kind of asymmetrical duel situation internationally between a majority of supporters and a minority of critics of the various state-imposed measures. It is a partly dramatic situation, it is a matter of life and physical as well as social death, which puts work and family relationships as well as friendships to the test and sometimes even causes them to break. Many even see it as a threat to social cohesion, because behind the heated controversy over how dangerous the virus is and how best to respond to it in a socially balanced way, fundamental issues are quickly at stake: attitudes toward life and community, toward the state, science, disease, healing and death. Thus, in the corona truth wars of individual countries, specific long-standing discourses intersect and condense. Based on participant observation and interviews with protesters this presentation will focus on the particularities of the controversy in Germany, and elaborate how old frontlines appear at the same time as completely new and unexpected social constellations emerge.

The Israeli Vaccination Campaign Through the Prism of Trust *Ori Freiman, Bar-Ilan University*

On December 20, the State of Israel began a vaccination campaign. To date, Israel has administered the most COVID-19 vaccine doses per capita, thereby becoming a world leader in vaccination. The willingness of the population to get vaccinated

and the consequent success of this campaign could be thought of as a knockout to corona deniers, anti-vaxxers, and those who intentionally spread misinformation about the vaccines. However, despite the success of Israel's vaccination campaign, many Israelis still hesitate or refuse to get vaccinated. Hesitancy and refusal are found at every demographic and political extreme, and have diverse causes. I analyze the Israeli vaccination campaign through the prism of trust. Instead of analyzing trust in the vaccination campaign as a whole, I identify a few objects of trust and show how they mostly fail to act in keeping with the interest of citizens. I examine trust relations with pharmaceutical companies, the US FDA, the Israeli government and health organizations, along with scientific institutions and new vaccination technologies. Despite common mistrust, distrust, and a lack of trust in these objects, another kind of trust plays a crucial role: trust that the vaccine is safe and works effectively. I contend that this type of trust can be increased by opening a dialogue with parties who refuse vaccines. Contra to the current refusal of Israeli mainstream media to give airtime to anti-vaxxers and hesitators, I argue that a discussion based on honesty, knowledge, and trust is the only democratic way to persuade vaccine-skeptics to take the plunge and get vaccinated.

PCR-Gate: Popular Contestations with Scientists and Media of the Gold Standard Measuring Corona Infections *Jaron Harambam, Institute for Media Studies - KU Leuven*

Since the coronavirus spread across the world, various suspicions and allegations proliferated about what is really going on. Some of these are far-fetched conspiracy theories, while others embody serious contestations to scientific truths and governmental policies. Polymerase Chain Reaction (PCR) tests became the gold standard to identify SARS-CoV-2 infections, and form the bedrock of (supra)governmental corona mitigation policies, which fluctuate along infection rates. The PCR test thus has great implications for the way the corona pandemic is managed, and how it disrupts everyday life. This very specific testing procedure gained much popular and (to a lesser degree) scientific critiques for a variety of reasons. These critiques range from not being able to identify infectious people as it only measures DNA remnants of the virus, to arguments that PCR testing is a massive fraud and part of a global conspiracy. In this paper, I analyze the interactions of laymen in the Netherlands propagating various PCR critiques with scientists and media who quickly responded to such conspiratorial claims as they reached massive audiences. How do these contestations take shape, what kind of (rhetorical) arguments are used to support/attack opponents, and what societal and scientific implications do they have? My empirical material is collected from a wide variety of sources: interview video's on YouTube, Twitter interactions, and mainstream news media reports. I conclude by arguing how these contentious interactions sow not just societal distrust, but also force scientists and media to be explicit and transparent about the workings of high-impact medical technologies.

Session Organizers:

Jaron Harambam, Institute for Media Studies - KU Leuven
Ehler Voss, University of Siegen

Discussant:

Linsey Jane McGoey

436. An Exquisite Corpse: Experiments in Practicing Better Relations as Scholars in Uncertain Times - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

The Exquisite Corpse (Le Cadavre Exquis, <https://www.artsy.net/article/artsy-editorial-explaining-exquisite-corpse-surrealist-drawing-game-die>) is a collaborative game of imperfect assemblage: each participant adds to a composition in sequence, not knowing or knowing little of what was added beforehand. In this panel, we deploy the “exquisite corpse” as a method and provocation for survival,

collaboration, and playful relations during these uncertain times, investing not in fixed outcomes but emergent relationships and knowledges. We invite anyone interested in an imaginative and experimental exercise, and in forging a liminal space of collaboration and solidarity, to join us in collectively creating an exquisite corpse. Individual submissions should not be traditional conference presentations but stories, poems, visualizations, or other narrative forms that center around research spaces unsettled by disturbances, quakes, fires, waters, or human catastrophe; timelines, career trajectories, research plans, budgets or any project plan disrupted in the face of trauma and uncertainty; relationships and bodies broken, brittle, and precarious. The only condition is that you leave your contribution open to articulation, re-pair, and imaginative attachments that can ferment unsuspected forms of sense-making, relationship-building, knowledge-production, and negotiation. Collectively, we will then assemble and draw connections that create multiple possibilities and outcomes for a more careful academic practice. Through the configuration of this exquisite corpse, we will explore the folds, redirections, and emergent properties that can generate good relations within the university and beyond.

Participants:

Exquisite Limbs: A Contribution to the Corpse *elizaBeth Simpson, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign*

Though “accessibility is a firm focal point” in arts-related research (Wimpenny and Savin-Badin, 2013) and a critical stance is counter-hegemonic and seeks to contribute to emancipatory knowledge (Madison, 2011) I have encountered plenty of (to me) cryptically written critical theory and apparently inaccessible presentations of arts-based outcomes. As a poet and lyricist. I soundly approve the manipulation of language for the sake of curating elicited meanings unavailable otherwise. However, as an outsider child who couldn’t get “in” to certain social spaces barred by linguistic and material “pass words” (e.g. at the time: penny loafers, Esprit clothing, and knowledge of certain pop culture forms) and who, in aspirational resonance, also cultivated cliquish practices to circumscribe a domain that I had sway over, I am familiar with the use of exclusionary language that may serve more to mark status than communicate knowledge. Brushing up against certain articulations in and near critical theory, I at times wonder whether some academic forms, even those which seek to “bring to light underlying and obscure operations of power and control” (Madison, 2011) are replicating exclusionary practices in their dissemination. Therefore, in the exposition of my form I want to maintain a careful eye to what is being composed in order to invite another into meaning; and what is composed in order to signify an insider perspective which may or may not also serve to obfuscate its contents such that onlookers without requisite references (here meant in terms of both literacy and credibility) won’t find enough purchase to either embrace or challenge it.

Umbrella Έλα 0.3 *Megan Olinger, City University of Hong Kong; Anton Dragan Maslic, City University of Hong Kong*

A group of PhD researchers selected a phrase or word(s) that necessitated (re)definition in their own projects. Using these as a springboard for sharing specific situated concepts, how might entanglement and support between diverse areas of knowledge production be uncovered by staying open to emergent relations? (re)cognizing recognition Is a non- a “深圳人 (Shenzhener) a 本地人 (local) or an 外地人 (outsider), who or what has agency of (re)cognizing recognition, enacting benevolence and efficacy, where are proximity and situation located, isn’t everything a STORY?! Neuroanatomical mechanisms as developed throughout evolution of the encephalon since the Cambrian explosion, is linking our somatic physiological existence with the construction of a metaphysical notion of reality and most peculiarly of storytelling from which we cannot escape. The brain continuously models a detailed world-simulation by processing a constant flow of sensory information, consequently creating an idealized protagonist it envisions itself to be. The self turns into an imagined avatar within a representational

constructed virtual reality, enabling speculations of the future to increase the likelihood of individual survival but also to safeguard the success of a species at large, generating as a by-product consciousness, within a (meta)narration of someone’s personally ‘written’ story. Placing an image into circulation serves as knowledge production and sharing. When distribution channels are increasingly corporatized and surveilled, visual communication relies even more heavily on what Ariella Azoulay calls the civil contract of photography, entrusting that a photographic event emerges into dispersant eventualities. Cognizant of the coded gaze, these “photo forms” (Hillenbrand 2020) shape-shift in order to evade and reveal with intent, coltish provocation, and gentle memorialization. A methodology of an exquisite corpse, allows for an interactive layering and sequencing of images in order to share latent meanings and experience, while engaging and critiquing the everyday established channels of distribution.

Fruitful Ruptures and Generative Instabilities: Inhabiting Non-Academic Scholarship *Amy Cox Hall*

Through an illustrated poem, I will explore the liminality of conducting research during a break in my decade long career working as a college professor. Instead of doubts or insecurities that might attend this rupture, non-university affiliated scholarship has been a release; a liberation full of possibility. Writing toward different audiences allows for creative play, altering receptivity of what counts as insight, as evidence, as worthy. Play alters my interactions, inviting me to nurture new relations, as I attend to non-academic worlds with open-ended potential. The fruitfulness of this fracture has been surprising; generating a sense of expansiveness for the kind of worlds we might create vis-à-vis the cleavage of disciplinary boundaries.

Umbrella Έλα 0.3 - Local embeddedness as potential for relating differently *Christine Maria Kaiser, School of Creative Media - City University Hong Kong; Anja Lückenkemper*

A group of PhD researchers selected a phrase or word(s) that necessitated (re)definition in their own projects. Using these as a springboard for sharing specific situated concepts, how might entanglement and support between diverse areas of knowledge production be uncovered by staying open to emergent relations? Is a non- a “深圳人 (Shenzhener) a 本地人 (local) or an 外地人 (outsider), who or what has agency of (re)cognizing recognition, enacting benevolence and efficacy, where are proximity and situation located, isn’t everything a STORY?! Foucault’s “Discursive Formations” and Anna Tsing’s “messy pile of junk” are assemblages that vary in their interpretative debate. In cultural comparison, phenomena that cannot be classified come to the fore and what is not understood is often dismissed as culture. It is important to question this claim to universality by bringing together people, things, ideas, voices and from the position of our local embeddedness with the intention of fostering a relation towards difference.

STS as Experience: Communicating Science Studies as an Act of Expression *Megan Halpern, Michigan State University*

This presentation is part of a larger research project to understand science communication in terms of Dewey’s theory of aesthetic experience, as outlined in *Art as Experience* (1936). The project invites scientists and scholars to consider their attempts to communicate science not as opportunities for dissemination of information, but rather, as acts of expression that offer audiences opportunities for experiences. Such acts, as Dewey describes them, begin with an “impulsion” or deep drive to explore and share something meaningful. Acts of expression are, in and of themselves, aesthetic experiences, and they often result in the creation of expressive objects. In turn, expressive objects created through acts of expression provide opportunities for audiences to have aesthetic experiences. This talk has two parts. In the first, I share my own experiences drawing on art and design to create

public engagement with STS events, as well as my work fostering collaborations among artists and scientists. Through this narrative, I describe my model for science communication in terms of expression and experience, drawing particular attention to the need to include public communication of STS scholarship in discussions of science communication. During the second part of the presentation, I engage participants and attendees in an improvisational activity designed to explore the nature of expression as Dewey describes it and to offer participants an opportunity to engage in acts of expression.

Session Organizers:

Jade Vu Henry, Goldsmiths, University of London

Lisa Lehner, Cornell University

Nadine Tanio, University of California, Irvine

437. Engaging Science, Technology and Society: Meet the Journal's Editorial Collective

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

In this session, meet and hear from Engaging Science, Technology, and Society's new transnational Editorial Collective (EC). ESTS, the Open Access (OA) journal of the Society for Social Studies of Science (4S), was launched in 2015 and quickly became a vibrant venue for publishing high-quality research in STS. This included experiments in short-form writing that worked to engage both scholarly and broader audiences. In this session, the journal's Editorial Collective -- whose members are based in Australia, Brazil, India, New Zealand, Turkey, the United Kingdom, and the United States -- will describe how we are building on this foundational work. The session will begin with a brief presentation on publishing priorities for the coming years; the editorial team's collective workflow practices; protocols to diversify our reviewer community; and initiatives to expand peer-reviewed genre-forms. We will also describe how the EC is working with other groups on issues related to scholarly publishing: our ongoing efforts to think through the politics of language in STS as a collective; and both challenges and possibilities presented by digital infrastructure. After briefly presenting on the journal's initiatives and practices, the EC will open the session up for questions and feedback, with the hope of facilitating a robust discussion with the 4S community.

Session Organizer:

Alison Kenner, Drexel University

Chairs:

Noela Invernizzi, Universidade Federal do Parana

Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University

Aalok Khandekar, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad

Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine

Grant Jun Otsuki, Victoria University of Wellington

Sujatha Raman, The Australian National University

Amanda Windle, Managing Editor, ESTS

Emily York, James Madison University

438. Beyond Solutionism for a Responsible Artificial Intelligence - I: Research Approaches

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

We propose a post-solutionist reflection on what is Responsible AI, to discuss interdisciplinary perspectives that contribute to making AI systems more fair, transparent, and inclusive. Solutionism is "recasting all complex social situations either as neat problems with definite, computable solutions or as transparent and self-evident processes that can be easily optimized if only the right algorithms are in place!" (Morozov 2013) Ethical problems in AI/ML have been exposed through numerous and influential publications (Buolamwini & Gebru 2018, Challen & al 2019, Parikh & al 2019, Yapo & Weiss 2018). How can we move from a view of ethics and responsibility narrowly focused on technical definitions of bias, discrimination, and fairness in AI systems to one which considers interconnecting issues of cognitive bias, social inequality, white supremacy, intersectionality, geopolitical and economic divides? A robust

consideration of ethics and responsibility requires that we interrogate how technologies are interwoven with our social structures, histories, and moral imaginations (Noble 2018; Benjamin 2019). We must go beyond tech solutionism to frame problems without automatically assuming AI/ML is the best or inevitable course of action, to fully explore fine-grain signals and our complete range of options, which can include refusal. Topics to be addressed in Session 1 include power and ubiquity of automated systems in daily life, over-trust in technical solutions, and whether our current research approaches support or hinder just and equitable AI systems.

Participants:

Using Institutional Ethnography to Study Embedded Values in AI Systems *James Shaw*, *Women's College Hospital*; *Andrew Buzzell*, *York University, Toronto*; *Joseph Donia*, *University of Toronto*; *Natasha Richmond*, *University of Toronto*

This paper explores the application of institutional ethnography (IE) to the study of AI development practice, specifically with the aim of uncovering the ways in which values are materialized in the production and deployment of AI systems. There is a growing awareness that AI systems frequently produce and reproduce inequities and oppressions. This is often caused by the data used, which can amplify existing inequities, but can also be caused by the ways in which biases become embedded in systems themselves; specifically, in the ways they construct, interpret, and deploy representations in sociotechnical systems, often with harmful social and ethical impacts. The development of AI involves complex institutional coordination and cooperation, mediated by textual artifacts generated by loosely networked institutions. What an AI system accomplishes, from the standpoint of people's actual experiences, often varies from how it is understood by developers. The methodology of IE is explicitly designed to explore this kind of problematic. In this presentation we outline how IE is well-suited to the investigation of values embedded in technology because it explicitly addresses the work practices and knowledges through which technology and its affordances are built. IE emphasizes adopting the standpoint of specific actors in the development context to represent the various tensions at play, and employs analysis of textual artifacts to reveal the complex relations that coordinate these experiences. IE methods uncover tensions, contradictions, and value misalignments at the junction of the performance of work and the institutional conditions that structure and shape how it is done.

Google Maps and Conditions of Accuracy *Rebecca Noone*, *University of Toronto*

Today, Google Maps is the answer to all location-based questions. Its data activates ride-sharing and food delivery while its predictive functionality suggests places to "experience". At the same time, Google Maps reconfigures space by way of renaming neighbourhoods, mislabeling sites, and misinterpreting viable routes (Dewey, 2019; Noble, 2018; Benjamin, 2019;). Automated location awareness seems inconsistent and at times incompatible with local knowledges, reducing location to a technology-centric idea of a singular, operational form. This paper considers the enclosures of accuracy within this automation of location awareness. First, I identify how Google Maps' inaccuracies are often shaped as comical mishaps—people following the directions into off-road predicaments (Kennedy, 2019). Though framed as trivial "errors", these incidents demonstrate how we are individually blamed for following Google Maps while at the same time Google Maps imposes a structural logic on space that prevents the possibility of "opting out" (i.e. even if you do not use the map, you are mapped). Google Maps distributes information through its API, operationalized through other platforms like Real Estate sites or Uber—thus setting the conditions of what accurate spatial representation is without an opt-out. I bring this dynamic to light through an analysis of resistance to Google Maps in Buffalo,

New York's Fruit Belt Neighbourhood (Dewey, 2019). Through this example and others, I argue that conditions of accuracy are determined not by space or local relations to space, but by what best serves the digital map itself. This paper examines the stakes of computational location awareness, revealing that searching with Google is more than just putting a database to work; it is a type of world-making in which space is a product of the map.

Making the unknown knowable: Designing 'good' technologies for cleaning up the UK's atomic legacy *Basak Saraç-Lesavre, The University of Manchester*

What does it entail to design 'good' robotic technologies for the cleaning up of the UK's atomic legacy? This is the question that the researchers at the RAIN (Robotics and Artificial Intelligence in Nuclear) Hub are grappling with. The RAIN Hub is a grouping of research laboratories that are designing robotic technologies for the cleaning up of the Sellafield nuclear site, which contains the UK's most hazardous atomic legacy. RAIN researchers often use the notion of the 'unknown' to characterize this peculiar site. However, they also use this notion to characterize their relationship to 'things nuclear'. Nuclear environments were previously unknown to most of them (mostly electrical/electronic engineers, control engineers, computer scientists, etc.), and encountering their particularities proved to be quite unsettling, including their concealed nature. While RAIN researchers conceived their technologies as 'solutions', concerned actors at Sellafield often qualified them as 'unsafe', and as 'potentially hostile', likely to disrupt the site's long-maintained state. In this sense, making Sellafield knowable relied on a series of, often contingent, political, regulatory, techno-scientific, temporal and financial arrangements, constantly negotiated with regulatory/governmental agencies, and industrial actors. This paper draws on an ethnographic research project conducted on this Hub, and unfolds the trials that their designs have undergone in their efforts to reach technologies construed as valuable and desirable to make these 'extreme environments' knowable and governable. It also discusses what this specific case tells us about the relationship between 'innovation' and 'maintenance'.

Octagon Scale: Measuring AI ethics *hiromi M. yokoyama; Yuko Ikkatai, The University of Tokyo*

AI has many ethical issues, including prejudice and discrimination. Up to now, there was no AI ethical scoring system. If there were a well-established ethics score in STS, it would help researchers and society understand ethical issues upstream of R&D. Over 38 AI guidelines have been proposed worldwide, from which eight general themes were extracted from these AI guidelines (Fjeld et al. 2020). We then propose an "octagon scale" based on these eight themes. Using the Octagon scale, we have prepared four scenarios to visualize the attitude of the general public towards AI ethics. These scenarios are designed to involve different types of ethical issues. The four AI scenarios are: performance of a dead singer, developing weapons with AI, predictive policing, and online shopping with recommender systems. This time, we investigated how society determines the ethical scores of these scenarios. Through online research, we found that whether we agree or disagree with the use of AI depends on the scenario, and we have gathered other relevant data. The Octagon Scale is very helpful in enabling effective discussions to understand how people feel about the risks of rapid penetration of technology, especially AI, and where the problem lies. Of course, the Octagon scale only partially visualises this. A deeper STS discussion is needed, but this attempt has the potential to revolutionize the AI ethics debate.

Session Organizers:

Katherine Fletcher, OpenStax at Rice University
Sarah Luger, Orange Silicon Valley

Chair:

Alexa Hagerty, University of Cambridge

Discussant:

Frederique Krupa, DIGITAL Design Lab, l'école de design Nantes Atlantique

439. STS Alter-ed: The Production of Otherness in Technoscientific Enactments (II)

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Michelle Murphy in her keynote address at the 2016 4S/EASTS meeting, "What a Body can't do?" called for STS to attend to alterlife—"a politics of entanglement, kinship, and responsibility" that explicates the material enmeshment of the human body with chemical exposures and environmental violence (7). She claims that bodies are already "more-than-bodies" and "they stretch outward to water, air, ancestors and other beings, that stretches backward to messy histories and forward to something else" (11). Today, we find ourselves in tense entanglements of exclusionist relationalities that reify the boundaries which frame the modern subject and their embodiment. Power structures including religion, racism, law, science, technology contribute to the production of otherness within a technoscientific apparatus like nuclear energy, AI, Big Data etc. (Ali). While STS has extensively focused on inclusion and exclusion of beings in technoscientific enactments, the philosophical, sociological, historical and anthropological treatment of the meanings of "alterity" or otherness that emerge under technoscientific duress remain unaddressed. Calling for an STS of alterity, this panel asks, 1) how and what constitutions of otherness, say human/non-human, is produced in technoscientific enactments? 2) how the boundaries and relations between self and other are made, unmade and reified through technoscientific enactments? 3) are these (alter-ed) relations racial, colonial, imperial, postcolonial, gendered? This panel aims to bring together a large array of research on technoscientific practices and how they produce "otherness." Papers that explicate the production of otherness in the context of environmental justice and contamination, especially radiation contamination, are particularly welcome. Papers may also interpret STS theories including Actor Network Theory (as called for the by Law), New Materialisms, (Crip) Feminist and anti-racist Technoscience using the frames of "othering" and "alterity." Bibliography Ali, Misria S. 2020. "Memorializing Decommissioning: A Nuclear Culture Approach to Safety Culture." *RSA Journal* 31 (2020): 33-58. Law, John. 2002. "Objects and Spaces." *Theory, Culture & Society* 19 (5-6): 91-105. doi:10.1177/026327602761899165. Murphy, Michelle. 2017 "What Can't a Body Do," *Catalyst* 3 (1): 1-15. https://catalystjournal.org/index.php/catalyst/article/view/28791/pdf_5

Participants:

Hybrid corn subsidy in Rocafuerte: the technofix that modified the territory and people's health *Mayra Alejandra Flores, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*

In 1980, the Ecuadorian National Institute for Agricultural Research (INIAP) created a program to develop hybrid corn meant to grow in the coastal region. Hybrid seeds promised to be a technological fix for several agricultural problems. Since then, public and private research brought to the market different varieties of hybrid seeds. In 2012, the government created a subsidy for hybrid corn in an effort to mediate between growers, animal feed manufacturers, and the meat industry. This increased monoculture landscapes and negatively impacted agricultural soil and people's health. One of the first places that signed up for the subsidy was Rocafuerte, a region in the province of Manabí. This paper ethnographically discusses how agricultural technologies modify landscapes, how we embody ecologies and its intertwining with health. It documents the transformation of corn seeds into a profitable resource on its way to the chicken feedlot while rearranging the socio-natural metabolism of Rocafuerte's territory and people. I situate the subsidy of seeds amid a political and economic dispute and argue that it rapidly generated complex unequal chemical exchanges that shape human and non-human interactions in place and time, of matter and meaning. I dialogue with peasants, epidemiologists, agricultural engineers, and geographers to problematize their conceptualizations of health, the borderlines between body and territory, agricultural

technologies, and toxic exposure.

The Poetics and Politics of Electronic Waste Infrastructure
Surojit Kayal, University of California, Santa Barbara

This paper examines the triangulation of electronics, waste and infrastructure in the constitution of alterity in a post-global world. Each of these categories, separately and in concert, I argue, reconfigure existing boundaries of self and other. The electronic extensions of man rewrite the boundaries of human and machine (Hayles 1999). Waste has always been a fraught ontological category that marks the limits of the self. From bodily products to undesirable populations, the modern subject has been quick to categorize and dispose of waste matter to retain its sense of identity and purity. An entire technosocial apparatus such as the caste system builds itself upon this ontological desire for purity. In a neoliberal economy, waste becomes both electronic and infrastructural (Gabrys 2013, Ty 2015). As part of transnational infrastructures, e-waste flows from developed centers to developing peripheries to contaminate the air, earth, water and bodies of poor people (Mukherjee 2020, Graeter 2020). Contamination, the supposed enemy of the western subject is disposed upon its others to maintain its ontological, material and political selfhood. My paper examines this triangulation through a reading of Chen Qiufan's sci-fi novel, *Waste Tide* (2013) which depicts the contaminated landscape of Silicon Isle, fictional equivalent of Guiyu, the capital of e-waste processing in Guangdong, China. Building upon existing scholarship from the emerging critical infrastructure studies, I propose in this paper a theory of infrastructural realism, which explains an aesthetic of representation, and also serves as an analytical category to map uneven geographies of self/other, center/margin, purity/contamination, and flow/dump.

Smart Cities and Urban Planning in India: The Sanitary City through Neo-liberal Means
Devika Prakash

This paper investigates how the smart city is understood and enacted by urban planners in India and how the smart city, in turn, influences practices of planning. Eight urban professionals, mainly urban planners, working on the Government of India's Smart Cities Mission were interviewed and an in-depth analysis performed on the official publications of the Smart Cities Mission. The paper advocates for focusing on situated practices of smart city making while acknowledging that the smart city is not a completely empty vessel that takes on contextual connotations, but is already associated with particular imaginaries of neoliberal market-based urbanism, and technology and data intensive development. The paper finds that urban planning practices in India still lean towards the positivist origins of planning and that practitioners form a rather elite and exclusive group. The Smart Cities Mission centers the role of planners in designing the city, but the planners are now located in private companies. In terms of planning practice, the smart city develops a vision of data intensive urban planning, in which the inhabitants of the city are imagined to be passive providers of a constant stream of data with which the planners could further optimise resource use in the city. By reinforcing the role of the technical expert and the integrated city, the smart city seems to be a return to the ideals of the Sanitary City of the late 19th and early 20th century but manifested through new interactions with private practice.

Mass-ive Protest: Petition, Assembly and Algorithmic Transparency
Kris Fallon, University of California, Davis

In their contribution to the recently revised Handbook of STS, Breyman et al. demonstrate the fundamental connection between STS and the larger social movements that arose alongside the discipline, what they describe as the "many activists, thinkers, and writers whose critiques of science and technology emerged in contexts of social struggle and conflict." Indeed, STS positions itself at the nexus of science and technology on one hand and the society to which it applies on the other. At the

center of this exchange lies the authority and institutional leverage of states, scientific disciplines and technology corporations against the collective, assembled power of everyday people. Recently, petition and assembly have been used to challenge state violence and the big tech corporations that enable it, protesting both immigration policy and policing in the US and pressuring companies to sever ties with the US government. This paper will consider the role of petition and assembly as a fundamental tool for shaping both state and corporate policy as well as specific research agendas in computer science and engineering. Drawing on political theory and the history of rights of petition, I will argue that what I call massive publics are both essential and anathema to the development of computer vision algorithms like Amazon's Rekognition tool. Such tools represent the state of the art in AI and computer vision (having trained on millions of images) and yet their use is controversial. Bowing to intense public pressure, Amazon temporarily barred police departments from using the technology, but in the absence of legal policy and sustained scrutiny, it remains unclear how lasting this victory will prove to be.

Session Organizer:

Dibyadyuti Roy, Indian Institute of Technology (IIT) Jodhpur

Chair:

Misria Shaik Ali, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Discussant:

Rahul Mukherjee, University of Pennsylvania

440. Caste as/of Technoscience - III

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Despite its continued importance as an analytical category in the social life of south asia, and south asians globally, caste as a lens or a category of analysis has historically remained relatively undertheorized in the social studies of science and technology. If at all, caste has largely figured as an identity category in extant work. Can reframing the study of caste as a study of technoscience improve our engagements with caste as a social category as well as that of the social study of science and technology? What conceptual and methodological toolkit would such a move need? How are caste and technoscience intertwined? Is caste an historically morphing assemblage which shapeshifts as new sociotechnical arrangements become possible/are enabled by it? If so, what new ways of thinking about caste are enabled when we approach 'caste' as technoscience? And vice versa, what new ways of thinking about technoscience are enabled as we think about 'technoscience' as caste? This panel invites papers that work with caste not only in axes of identity vis a vis technoscientific worlds but also think through caste as technoscience. These may range from case studies of sociotechnical assemblages that converge around different kinds of "work," debates around labour and caste relations, discursive efforts towards castelessness in the name of "merit," to theoretical pieces that reflect on methodological concerns on the matter which address the co-construction and reification of the caste system through technoscientific practices, imagination and rhetoric in different communities of South Asia and its diaspora.

Participants:

(Un)Making A Manual Scavenger: The Co-ordering Of Caste And Contract In Bengaluru, India
Shreyas Sreenath, Bowdoin College

This paper ethnographically traces how Bengaluru's inhabitants live and die amid the unruly flows of modern sewerage. It asks how caste and contractual liberalism share a common necropolitical interest in fickle socio-technical systems. In contemporary Indian cities, sewage infrastructures have become sites for the reinvention of manual scavenging, a legally abolished caste practice that degrades and kills ostracized communities by exposing them to human excreta. Thousands of Dalit (ex-untouchable) and contractual workers have died attempting to clear blockages in the same sewage lines that promise liberal modernity to an urbanizing populace. Elaborating

on recent cases in Bengaluru, a major metropolis touted as India's Silicon Valley, I detail how incidents escape legal purview as manual scavenging is increasingly framed as an accidental effect of unruly sewage flows. While recent studies have highlighted the modalities that caste power takes within liberal discourses of merit, modernity, and constitutional rights, few have explored the co-constitution of liberalism and caste within more-than-human systems operating under ecological duress. Detailing how mundane social and technical slippages in Bengaluru's sewerage accrue to maim and humiliate certain caste communities, I argue that the co-ordering of caste and contractual power crafts more-than-human toxicities into extra-human alibis, cultivating caste-blind subjectivities within the same systems that systematically reproduce caste degradation.

Technologies of Development and Managerial Conceptions of Productivity: Caste in Histories of Rural Development *Kena Wani*

This paper will study a set of techno-managerial experiments in the rural regions of western India between the 1950s-1970s, and its attempts at reforming the rural peasantry through the formation of cooperative societies, self-help programmes, as well as televisual pedagogy. I will show how these projects attempted to come to terms with the hierarchies of caste when they chose to intervene in them, and the 'unintended' outcomes that were occasioned in the process. The paper will follow the trajectories of a team of managerial experts and developmental pedagogues, and examine their frameworks of rural development in the first three decades following independence. I will show how these interventions constituted a specific imagination of a 'village society' which could be improved through the methodologies of the then emerging social sciences of 'group studies' and 'behavioural studies'. In this new vocabulary of social sciences, the 'group' was consistently seen as a resource of social capital that could be utilized for further enhancing and stimulating rural productivity. Further, the projects were invested in 'skilling' the peasantry through new technologies and 'behavioural' changes that could bring the rural society in alignment with market forces. My paper will show how caste hierarchies inevitably became a limit condition against which such ideas of socio-economic reform had to step back, and often fold up. And how, within the 'problem solving' orientation of managerial expertise, this 'limit' continued to throw open new 'solutions' and reformist visions, generating peculiar developmentalist conceptions of caste vis-à-vis productivity in the process.

Race, Caste, and the Robotic Future *Hemangini Gupta, Middlebury College*

What is a robot? This talk draws on long-term ethnographic fieldwork in Bangalore, India's technology city, to show how technologists and entrepreneurs design and imagine creative inventions—like the robot—to imagine a postcolonial future. Centering the robot as a particular kind of technological object, this paper suggests that the idea of freedom articulated by entrepreneurs in Bangalore is both haunted by the racialized laboring figure of the cyber "coolie" (or indentured laborer) and articulated through a matrix of colonial difference in which freedom attaches itself to a mobile body. My fieldwork shows how caste does not emerge within technoscientific startup capitalism as a category of identity but in and through imaginations of labor, creativity, and transnational mobility. This paper contributes to contemporary STS conversations around racialized imaginations of the human (Vora and Atanasoski 2019, Jackson 2020), robotic imaginaries (Rhee 2018), and conditions of postcolonial technoscientific experimentation (Irani 2019, Thomas 2018).

Session Organizer:

Palashi Vaghela, Cornell University

Discussant:

Renny Thomas, Department of Humanities and Social

Sciences, IIISER Bhopal, India

441. Climate change and the governance of time - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Participants:

After "After Geoengineering": Time and Technology in an Uncertain Future *Alexander Jenseth, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute - STS*

Futures and time are integrally linked with discourses of climate change; discussions of plausible alternatives to present projections necessarily invoke deep questions regarding the relationship between past-present-future. Though this holds for any specific point of discussion, geoengineering has emerged as an especially complex example of governance and time intersecting. Using the recent publication of "After Geoengineering: Climate Tragedy, Repair, and Restoration" (2019), by Holly Jean Buck, this paper aims to examine a still somewhat nascent shift among thinkers on the left and in the humanities/social sciences toward a cautious/skeptical embrace of "geoengineering" and the various implications and assumptions included in such calls. Though these calls tend to differ considerably from the usual image of the benevolent supervillain seizing control of the climate, Buck and others force us to consider every option; speaking of our present, she asks: "If this is one degree [rise above the norm], what will three degrees be like? Four?" (1) Buck and others in this discussion take seriously the very real possibility of such schemes being--though not preferable--vitaly necessary to avoid a "four degree future," particularly for the "front lines" of global climate crisis. She is not alone in asking these questions, and this paper will take the opportunity to examine scholarship that fits this "cautious embrace" such as the Strelka Institute's program, and the supplemental short book by Benjamin Bratton explaining its premise, *The Terraforming* (2019), and the edited volume from Buck, Andreas Malm, and J.P. Sapinski, "Has it Come to This? The Promises and Perils of Geoengineering on the Brink" (2020), among others, pulling out some lingering questions and assumptions made about time.

Carbon Neutral Discourses In Montreal: How To Act Today With 2050 In Mind *Hélène Madénian, Institut national de la recherche scientifique*

As many other cities around the world, the City of Montreal aims at being carbon neutral by 2050. Carbon management, i.e. quantifying and reducing GHG emissions, becomes a central issue in the fight against climate change and a new tool for economic competitiveness (Jonas, Gibbs and While 2011). However several discourses concerning the carbon neutral city emerge in parallel, with a trend towards technological fixes and innovation as solutions (Kenis and Lievens 2017, Tozer and Klenk 2018). In this paper, I want to explore how certain discourses play a role on the capacity to act today for 2050. My theoretical framework combines literatures on discourse, policy mobility and the sociology of expectations. The concept of "story-line" enables us to understand the different narratives and how they gather actors (Hajer 1997). STS provides insights for understanding the challenges linked to a carbon neutral city by considering the expectations linked to technologies and their potential in the future (July 2015; Konrad et al. 2017). The policy mobility literature analyses how "best practices" are often mobilized, imitated, adapted and reused in various cities (McCann 2013, Crivello 2015). The methodology of this qualitative research project combines document analysis and interviews with actors taking part in the city climate policy process, its implementation but also dissenting voices. My goal is to understand which discourses dominate and why, and identify tensions in climate policies. My contribution is to shed a new light on urban climate governance by documenting actors'

expectations towards a carbon neutral future.

Changes in climate risk regulation over time *olivier chanton, IRSN*

The 2003 heat wave was a major event for the nuclear industry in France. In particular, it led the main stakeholders involved in nuclear safety regulation (the Nuclear Safety Authority, the Institute for Radiation Protection and Nuclear Safety, and Electricité de France) to reexamine the way they assess the impacts of extreme air and water temperatures on the design and operation of nuclear power plants, which had been little or not taken into account when they were designed in the 1970s. More broadly, the 2003 heatwave led to question the possible and various effects of climate change: longer and more intense heat waves, but also severe low water levels, increased risk of fire, etc., and their impact on the safety of nuclear power plants. These questions have direct connections to the way the future is made predictable, and in particular to the tools and methods that make it possible to calculate and predict the frequency and intensity of extreme events that could threaten French nuclear power plants over the coming decades. We will show that the evolution of these tools and methods resulted in a hybridization of two distinct time regimes. The changes under consideration put to the test a plurality of institutional arrangements, practices and ideas that constitute the core of the regulatory regime as it has been historically constructed and stabilized. These evolutions took differentiated forms depending on the existence of a more or less constraining technological "déjà-là". The changes observed affect not only the tools and knowledge mobilized to regulate nuclear risks but also the institutional arrangements and routines used for risk (re)assessment, in particular the practices of temporalization of regulation and their time horizons. The changes initially consisted in articulating different knowledge about the past and the present through incremental hybridizations of two distinct scientific tools, specifically: in the one hand, statistical modelling and extrapolation based on extreme past events and, in the other hand, climate modelling and forecasting. These changes also led to controlled and careful reconfigurations of existing institutional devices rather than to innovations or organizational and institutional radical shifts. These solutions aim to propose a specific framework for (re)assessing the risks associated with climate change. This specific framework articulates (try to) the specific institutional agenda and tools of climate change governance with the existing institutional agenda and tools of nuclear safety regulation in a specific time-framework. Concerning nuclear power plants under development and construction, that is when the sociotechnical constraints are easing, the transformations underway appear more radical and affect the tools used to think about the future and predict the threats that could affect nuclear safety in a more radical way and over longer time horizons of regulation. Climate models and the corresponding scientific infrastructures put in place since the 1990s to understand the effects of climate change are thus set to play a central role. Greenhouse gas emission scenarios and the distinctive time horizons of climate modeling are used. Our analysis highlights the complexity and difficulties inherent to the transformations initiated after the 2003 heat wave. It illustrates how the nuclear regulatory regime try to articulate its own pace, institutional temporalities and time horizons with those of the climate regulatory regime.

Good transitions? The multi-scale and temporal-infrastructural work of MITE *Claudio Coletta, University of Bologna*

The sustainable transition pathways deployed globally to meet the targets of reducing CO2 emissions by 2030 struggle to keep the pace of the "new climatic regime", its complexities and uncertain temporalities. Commonly considered as a passage from a state to another, I argue that the governance of transitions involves both shaping and to synchronizing multiple time dimensions to establish good relations between the current situations and the future ones. How good and for whose futures?

I will follow the action of the recently established Italian Ministry for Ecological Transitions (MITE) as a specific multi-scale temporal-infrastructural assemblage. In fact, MITE activity started announcing the need of a "pace-change" to tackle the "non-linear" nature of the climate crisis. MITE comes with a strong mandate: first, it will lead the inter-ministry committee for ecological transition, granted by a significant part of the Next Generation EU Fund's Italian share; secondly, it will adopt a cross-sectoral, cross-disciplinary and multi-level approach to coordinate a highly fragmented agenda. I will investigate the socio-technical governance arrangements produced by MITE also in relation with the European Green Deal, especially looking at the temporal work and the tuning-up practices amid the multiple and embedded time interferences. This way, I aim to contribute to a temporal and material understanding of the interactions between political agendas, organizational processes, technoscientific practices, and the deep time of environmental transformations.

Session Organizer:

Victor Toom, Netherlands Scientific Council for Government Policy (WRR)

442. Unpacking biosocial approaches to stress & trauma - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

This panel will bring together scholars researching trauma and stress from biosocial perspectives. Trauma-informed approaches are often positioned as a gold standard of care across biomedical, therapeutic, carceral and policy domains. Historical trauma frameworks have long been central to collective identity and politics among Indigenous, Black and other racially marginalised communities, and have gained momentum through recent anti-racist and anti-colonial movements like Black Lives Matter and Idle No More. Research fields like social epidemiology, critical public health and biological anthropology have explored how trauma and stress "get inside" the body to shape health disparities (e.g. "minority stress"; "weathering" [Geronimus 1992]). Recently, research on the developmental origins of health and disease and epigenetics is redefining trauma as an exposure with a heritable trace (Dubois&Guaspere 2020), raising new questions about ancestral memory and reproductive politics. We invite scholars from various disciplines to explore how trauma and stress are enacted biosocially through human experience, activist tactics, government policy and scientific knowledge. How are trauma and stress defined, studied and reformulated across these arenas? What are the social and political stakes of trauma-informed practices? What forms of temporality, identity and justice do they produce?

Participants:

Traumatic toxins: The Adverse Childhood Experiences Study, stressed environments and the origins of childhood abuse
Angelica Clayton, Yale University

This paper will examine how the Adverse Childhood Experiences study in the 1990s refashioned conversations around childhood trauma, the body and systemic racism. ACEs was a collaboration between the health care company Kaiser Permanente and the CDC which linked early traumatic experiences to physical ailments in adulthood, like heart disease or diabetes, as well as mental health and behavioral struggles, like alcoholism. While the repressed memory controversy was raging across the United States, ACEs proposed a model of trauma that suggested childhood abuse was a public health concern and, more specifically, a toxin that needed to be measured and eradicated. ACEs used language from toxicology to present childhood abuse as external to the individual and as something that defied the material-immaterial binary, accumulating in and passing unseen between bodies. This paper will bring together critical black studies, disability studies and STS to demonstrate how ACEs scaled-up existing frameworks for thinking about childhood trauma, violence and responsibility. Was there something inherently "toxic" about racialized communities with higher incidences of ACEs or did "abuse as

toxin” push researchers to focus on the structural and environmental circumstances that created the abuse? How did ACEs question the family as the necessary site of trauma-intervention by simultaneously emphasizing the home environment and public health dimension of this societal ill? And finally, how did the focus on public health emphasize preventative measures, which in turn created a rationale for neglecting those in the criminal justice system who had already felt and suffered the impact of ACEs?

Staging and Framing Adversity in Longitudinal Birth Cohort Studies *Sahra Gibbon, University College London*

As central ‘technologies of’ biosocial science (Gibbon and Pentecost 2019) longitudinal birth cohort studies provide a key terrain and social context for examining how biosocial approaches to trauma and stress are being constituted, with a particular notable focus on early childhood adversity, situated in terms of Adverse Childhood Experience (ACE). Drawing on collaborative cross-disciplinary conversations within a newly formed network of social scientists and epidemiologists that brings together those working with or on birth cohorts (Biosocial Birth Cohort Research Network) and preliminary scoping research linked to an international comparative study, examining the ‘Biosocial Lives of Birth Cohorts’ (in the UK, Portugal, Brazil and the Netherlands) I present some initial reflections on how questions of adversity are being defined, examined and measured in studies involving diverse longitudinal birth cohort studies. I outline how this entails particular framings of trauma or stress, as well as specific ways of staging and periodizing the life course. I reflect further on questions of standardisation in efforts to compare and measure adversity in birth cohorts whilst also addressing how these developments provide novel opportunities and challenges for cross-disciplinary collaboration in researching novel biosocial approaches to stress and trauma.

Thinking with “Biopossibility”: an Anti-disciplinary Approach to the Study of Embodiment and Experience *Samantha M Archer, University of Connecticut*

Sociocultural and medical anthropologists have utilized phenomenological frameworks of embodiment and experience as formulated by scholars such as Merleau-Ponty (1964) and Mauss (1979) for several decades now (Csordas 1990, Desjarlais and Throop 2011). With the advent of critical medical and biocultural anthropology, scholars have increasingly attended to questions of embodiment alongside the potential medical and biological effects of structural inequalities and violence (Goodman and Leatherman 1998, Singer 2004). Biological anthropologists and public health scholars have also called for the study of the embodied effects of structural violence on the individual and population levels (Geronimus 1992, Krieger 2005, Gravlee 2009). And more recently, since the uptick of studies in human epigenomics, scholars from diverse disciplines have demonstrated interest in the molecular correlates of violence and trauma (Lock 2013, Hoke and McDade 2014, Smith 2015, Thayer and Non 2015, Warin et al. 2020). In order to avoid the all-too-familiar pitfalls of deterministic thinking, we must co-think with one another and develop critical and integrative concepts of embodiment and experience against the disciplinary grain. Working from the scholarly genealogy of the study of embodiment and experience, this paper will first demonstrate the diversity of thought in the bodies of work briefly detailed here. I will then demonstrate more recent calls for a critical approach to the epigenomics of structural violence (Schuller 2018, Jackson 2020). Lastly, thinking with Angie Willey’s concept of “biopossibility,” this paper will explore what it might mean to approach these critically important questions through an ethic of anti-disciplinarity (Willey 2016).

Sensing Trauma: A Biosocial Exploration of Sexual Assault Memories *Sarah MacLean, Carleton University*

In 2019, Chanel Miller, the sexual assault survivor in the

infamous Stanford rape case, released a memoir detailing her journey through the entanglement of medico-legal procedures that followed her sexual assault. She highlights that the period following a sexual trauma is sensorially-rich, including her “brutal awakening” (Miller, 2019, p. 7) immediately following the assault, the forensic examination, and court proceedings. Previous literature has focused on the many ways the survivor body is sensed following a sexual assault. Sameena Mulla (2017), for instance, investigates how the forensic nurse translates the sensory experience of survivors “into the form of a primarily visual legal artifact” (p. 196). However, what is left out of this conversation is the survivor’s experience of “double sensation” (Merleau-Ponty, 1968), in which they are both the subject and object of sensing. This paper argues that one of the primary ways in which this is articulated is through sense memories, defined by Verbeek & van Campen (2013) as “the intensive reliving of events from the past through sensory stimulus” (p. 135). While these scholars, citing Marcel Proust, ground their arguments in the field of art and aesthetics to explore how sense memories embody the “joy of remembering” (Verbeek & van Campen, 2013, p. 135), this paper asks: what about when sense memories are not joyful? To answer this question, I bring together the fields of neuroscience and sensory studies to explore the nexus of trauma and memory to theorize how, in the period post-sexual assault, the traumatized body senses back.

Too Close for Comfort: Nurses and their ‘presumptive risk’ of PTSD *Shoshana Deutch, Cornell University*

In 2018, nurses in Ontario, Canada were officially recognized as “first responders” and included in legislation that also declared nurses at “presumptive risk” of Posttraumatic Stress Disorder (PTSD). Distinctive in how it is defined, identified, and diagnosed, PTSD often invokes a relationship between a traumatic cause and symptomatic effect; it has therefore been leveraged as a mechanism for restitution and restorative justice, utilizing the authority of medical practice to make real violence and suffering (Kirmayer et al 2007). For nurses, the legislation presented a means of “making real” and denaturalizing their experiences of everyday violence, stress, and trauma, even as it provided nurses none of the same protections and preventative measures as those provided to other first responders (i.e., firefighters, paramedics, police officers). By delving into how nurses become “at risk of PTSD” and the specific kinds of institutions, practices, knowledges, and absences that emerge in relation to it, this paper explores how PTSD has emerged as a means of evoking, explaining, and transforming the highly specialized and risky work of knowing and caring for patients in a frequently undermined and undervalued gendered profession like nursing. I employ ethnographic methods and discourse analysis to engage critically with the ways in which a highly contested illness like PTSD has become crucial for not only revealing the specific kinds of trauma and stress experienced by nurses, but also used to make known the often invisible and highly risky techniques, skills and practices demanded by nurses’ frequent and close proximity to patients.

Session Organizers:

Jaya Keaney, Deakin University
Emma Kowal, Deakin University
Henrietta Byrne, The University of Adelaide
Megan Warin, University of Adelaide

Chair:

Jaya Keaney, Deakin University

443. Critical Computational Relations of Design, Architecture and the Built Environment - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Living Architecture and micro-utopia: adaptive design and enacted semantics of form, movement and scenic morphologies *Andreea Felciuc, Ion Mincu University of Architecture and Urbanism Bucharest Romania*

The contemporary landscape of architecture, arts and culture is pushing towards participatory and immersive forms of performance. Can architecture intergrade living functions? What are the fundamental qualities that living architecture might offer? The kinetic morphologies of adaptive and scenic protoarchitecture are based on the architectural and performing space analysis and development. The human relationship with architecture could be transformed by contributing with a kind of 'agency' that creates active conversations and exchanges with their occupants, greatly enhancing the quality, the economic value, and the technical performance of the built environment. Inspired by the sensibilities and dynamic of natural systems, the new adaptive design will engage directly with the surrounding environment and go beyond the built environment's aspiration of neutrality. Protoarchitecture does not yet exist as a tool that can be applied. These interactive installations – part creature, part environment, part mechanical, part biological – remind us that the point of reference for architecture has shifted from the human to non-human. This research's future direction is defined by synthetic metabolic design and analysis on how adaptive and scenic morphologies are part of the next-generation architecture, addressing the role of semi-living design as a mediator between artists and audience.

Digital Architecture Research and the Enactment of Aesthetics *Esther Dessewffy, University of Vienna; Sarah R Davies, University of Vienna*

This paper explores the political dimensions of digital simulation in architecture. It speaks to STS literature that has discussed the role of digital tools and infrastructures in the crafting of societal relations (e.g. Vinck and Camus 2019, Star 1999). Digital Architecture promises standardizable procedures that allow architects to experiment with a building's stability, utility and aesthetics through simulations. The starting point for this paper is that paying attention to architects' enactments of aesthetics in such simulations is crucial for gaining insight into how architects draw conclusions about the relation between form and function, and also how they account for human experiences of future buildings. Given that these designs are often materialised, becoming part of our built environments, examining architects' enactments of aesthetics via simulation is a prerequisite for understanding the visions of the social that guide construction, and for identifying aspects that are not accounted for. Exploring practices that enact aesthetics might even teach us about the capacity of aesthetics to invoke new forms of political subjectivity (Porter 2009). The contemporary controversy over the tension between 'academization' and 'artistry' in academic architecture research (Kurath 2015) has meant that prevailing standards of practice and aesthetics are currently up for debate, offering STS research a glimpse into their ongoing negotiation. This paper contributes to examination of these negotiations by discussing the Viennese academic context of Digital Architecture Research, drawing on data from events, interviews and documents to outline how aesthetics are enacted and contested within this field.

CAD optimism: How Architects interested in Media and Computation Talk about Design *Selena Savic, Academy of Art and Design, FHNW*

"Great new design" is a phrase that emerges from simple counting of words in social media discourse among architects and designers working with computation and interactive technologies. With an underlying concern for the narrative of optimism and efficiency that propagates in practice of working with CAD tools, I study the way Media Architecture is discussed within the community of architects, designers, researchers and

policy makers. The bi-yearly event, Media Architecture Biennale, organised by the Media Architecture Institute gathers a large community of architects, designers and engineers interested in using and understanding computational tools in the context of design of media architecture (and media facades more specifically). I combine text-mining techniques of Twitter posts with practical knowledge of architectural profession and review of computational concepts in literature (Dalsgaard et al, Tomitsch et al, Brynskov et al but also Easterling, Bratton and Parisi). Using some of the digital humanities techniques, I identify a network of social media profiles that belong to architects, engineers, community managers and policy makers, with a mixed presence of practitioners and academics. I identify important concepts and patterns in this prolific communication stream, which I then critically examine through the way these conversations, literature and practice inform each other. I take social media as a rich, and digitally documented communication channel that relies on a multitude of media and forms. What can we infer from opinions on digital infrastructures, networked places and hybrid public spaces about their implications for practice of architecture, and methods architects use in design? Which occlusions and blind spots can be observed in the discourse? By looking at how contemporary practice is discussed, we can identify and offer a critical perspective on certain social and cultural aspects within the community.

Re-configuring Knowledge Infrastructures Through Building Information Modelling *Réka Andersson, Business administration, Department of Management and Engineering, Linköping university; Maria Eidenskog*

Building information modelling (BIM) is argued to create a revolution within the construction industry through more efficient use of resources and heightened interprofessional collaborations. Although BIM has been accessible for decades, it has yet not managed to become the standard industry method in practice. Based on workshops and interviews with professionals working with BIM, we argue that this is partly due to the destabilization of knowledge infrastructures that BIM creates. BIM challenges traditional knowledge hierarchies, as the technology privileges the latest technical competence to other types of knowing. Senior professionals with long working life experience, but limited competence in BIM, have problems to fully adapt to this new technology, as it is not suited to their purposes and imposes limitations to their expertise. In contrast, younger professionals have their basic education in BIM, which gives them a technical advantage, but due to less working experience their knowledge of the overall building process is limited. Consequently, BIM is an example of how technology is not neutral, as it makes conflicting knowledge infrastructures visible and changes power relations. While the latest technology can bring opportunities of new knowledge and optimization, its usefulness can be questioned if it destabilizes established knowledge infrastructures and thus creates conflicts.

Session Organizers:

Yana Boeva, University of Stuttgart

Vernelle A Noel, Georgia Institute of Technology

Chair:

Yana Boeva, University of Stuttgart

444. Making Early Career Researchers' Voices Heard for Gender Equality I: Institutional Policies and Initiatives

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

This first session explores how the specific gender inequalities and discrimination challenges faced by Early Career Researchers are addressed by equality policies and initiatives in research producing organizations and research funding organizations across Europe. Presentations intend to share good practices and lessons learned from institutional and individual experiences.

Participants:

Early Career Researchers: the Blind Spot of Gender Equality Policies *Anne-Sophie Godfroy, République des savoirs (CNRS, École Normale Supérieure, Collège de France); Areti Damala, CNRS and ENS - REPUBLIQUE DES SAVOIRS -PROJET ACT; Chloé Mour, CNRS USR 3608*

This paper is inspired by the workshops on the challenges faced by Early Career Researchers (ECRs) organized in December 2020 and January 2021 by the Community of Practice « Strategies for Sustainable Gender Equality » in collaboration with EURODOC, the European Council of Doctoral Candidates and Junior Researchers, under the framework of the EU-funded research project ACT (www.act-on-gender.eu). Our research scope is « gender equality plans » (GEPs) implemented in a large number of European universities. These plans follow both EU and national recommendations when they exist. Because of their frequent mobility and often short-term contractual status, ERCs are the blind spot for equality policies. At the same time, it is during early career stages that ERCs experiment with major gender equality challenges as parenthood and the injunction to mobility are indeed more complex to manage for female ERCs, among all other challenges. First, we examine the situation of ERCs in the "GEAR Tool", a reference toolkit proposed by the European Institute for Gender Equality to help institutions set up equality plans. This guide has been built on the good practices identified in all EU countries. Second, we analyze the action plan of Université Paris-Est Créteil as a case study, in order to understand where the blind spots are, both in terms of indicators and implemented measures. Finally, we conclude by proposing some measures that would allow better consideration of ERCs' gender equality concerns and by suggesting some research topics on little-documented challenges faced by ERCs.

Abstract: Enhancing the 'i' of Inclusion: The 6i+ Strategy as an Institutional Policy Driver. *Antonia Caro Gónzalez, University of Deusto; María López Belloso, University of Deusto; María Silvestre, University of Deusto; Irene García Muñoz, University of Deusto*

While faced with the challenge of ensuring better career prospects and development for Early Stage Researchers (ESR), higher education institutions are confronted with twofold defiance: enhancing inclusion and properly addressing the gender dimension. All these within conventional contexts that present resistance to change. At the University of Deusto, a medium size non-research intensive university in the Basque Country, Spain, a flexible multi-layered intervention process, the 6i+ Strategy, aiming at institutional purpose-driven coordinated initiatives (Caro, 2018; Caro & Ferreira-Lopes, 2019; Caro & Anabo, 2020), has played a key role in vertebrating institutional policies and mechanisms to ensure better career prospects and development within and outside academia. It strategically integrates multiple dimensions that traditionally suffer from a piecemeal approach: (1) internationalisation, (2) interdisciplinarity, (3) intersectorality, (4) impact, (5) innovation, and (6) inclusion. The 6i+ Strategy understands inclusion as the participation of people with different identities, origins and from different social groups who contribute to the education and research processes with their unique perspectives (Fonseca, Caro, Milosevic (2020) clearly in line with intersectional approaches proposed by feminism (Crenshaw, 2017). This paper will analyse the different managerial levels that the 6i+ Strategy has unfolded to address and reinforce the gender institutional policies and the impact that this policy could have in ESRs examining the experience of the "6 IDIRS COFUND project".

Mentoring Women in Science in France *Julie BATUT, Centre de Biologie Intégrative (FR 3743), MCD (UMR5077), CNRS, Univ; Marina KVASKOFF, Paris-Saclay University,*

UVSQ, Univ. Paris-Sud, Inserm, Gustave Roussy; Géraldine LIOT, CEA/FAR, University Paris-Saclay; Julie MENETREY, CNRS –Gif-sur-Yvette, University Paris-Saclay; May MORRIS, IBMM CNRS UMR5247; Colette GUILLOPE, Université Paris-Est Créteil

The proportion of female and male students studying science at French Universities is similar and young women are not afraid to engage in scientific studies in most fields. However, throughout their doctoral studies, female scientists tend to lose confidence and question their skills and professional future. A lack of incentive to pursue a scientific career beyond the PhD is in large part associated with a lack of support, encouragement and guidance. To address these issues and provide female scientists with female role models in science in the early years of their career, Femmes & Sciences, a French Association that promotes science and technology, and further supports women throughout their scientific careers, has established a mentoring programme that provides a trustworthy and nurturing environment to discuss their career path and learn to value their skills with a stimulating network of experienced scientific mentors. The originality of this pioneering French programme driven by an association of voluntary female scientists at the interface between doctoral schools and research laboratories lies in the subtle combination of individual and collective meetings, including regular meetings between a mentee and a mentor over a one-year period, mentoring circles that bring together several mentees and mentors who debate on specific issues, career development workshops, and presentations by female scientists selected as role models to inspire younger generations. The programme is now well established in Montpellier, Toulouse and Paris-Saclay, and likely to be extended to other French cities in the near future, given its impact and success.

Gender mainstreaming in Swedish science funding: A study of sex and gender perspectives in grant proposals *Karolin Sjö, Chalmers University of Technology; Wolfgang Kaltenbrunner*

Science funding bodies in many countries have begun to incorporate gender mainstreaming strategies into their funding instruments. This also includes incentives for grant seekers to address sex/gender perspectives on the level of the substantive content of the proposed research projects. But while these types of policies are increasingly common, relatively little is known about their effects. The majority of existing studies simply aim to quantify explicit references to policy-defined aims in project proposals (such as explicit mentioning of sex/gender dimensions). This reflects a long tradition of undertheorized thinking in science policy making, where governance is thought of as a matter of applying instruments whose "impacts" are straightforwardly identifiable. In this paper, we present results of a qualitative content analysis of 228 STEM research proposals submitted to the Swedish Research Council which, starting in 2020, requires all applicants within these fields to consider the integration of the sex/gender perspective. Conceptually, we analyze gender mainstreaming incentives in science funding as an affordance, that is, their perception and realization is shaped by the particular epistemic and practical conditions under which applicants work. We also assume that researchers are likely to choose the path of least resistance in addressing sex/gender dimensions in their applications, and that we should therefore expect a spectrum of possibilities for achieving alignment between the funding mandate and the research proposed. Our empirical analysis will characterize different strategies of integrating sex/gender and identify patterns that help explain why particular strategy types appear "doable" to applicants in particular areas of research.

Session Organizer:

Anne-Sophie Godfroy, République des savoirs (CNRS, École Normale Supérieure, Collège de France)

Chair:

Arèti Damala, CNRS and ENS - REPUBLIQUE DES SAVOIRS -PROJET ACT

Discussant:

Chloé Mour, CNRS USR 3608

445. Frameworks of responsibility that reshape food systems - I: Agrifood knowledge infrastructures

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

This is the first of two sessions dedicated to understanding frameworks of responsibility that have transformative potential for food systems. This session will open with the presentation of an emerging framework for responsibility that draws upon notions of environmental justice and responsible research and innovation. The papers in this session touch upon responsabilisation of scientists and citizens.

Participants:

Responsibilising food system innovations: 'Doing' food waste in China *Emma Xueshi Li*, Michigan State University; *Allison Marie Loconto*, INRAE

A large gap in the literature on food systems concerns those actors working in the middle between production and consumption processes. (e.g., transporters, processors, traders, wholesalers, retailers, food service and catering). While these actors have long been using standards and certifications to govern their suppliers and communicate to consumers, the standards have remained mostly focused on evaluating the sustainability of production, not of the processing, trade and patterns of consumption that the intermediaries engage. This paper closes the gap by examining how actors working in the middle of food systems may take on collective responsibilities to ensure that food is not wasted, and thus sustainable consumption patterns can emerge. We draw upon recent theories of responsible innovation and community studies to understand how University communities in Shenzhen, China are developing actions in reducing food waste. A mixed method study (content analysis, supply chain analysis Q-method and ethnographies) was used to understand how delivery companies, university cafeterias and students and staff who cook for themselves are 'doing' food waste on campus. This paper contributes to STS concerns with doings and the relational foundations for these doings.

Slow Expertise for a Quick Counting: Wild birds and Human Census Surveyor's Response-ability in the Winter Waterbird Census of South Korea *Hanah Sung*, Seoul national univ.

This paper explores expertise required in counting birds for the Winter Waterbird Census, the largest survey of wild animals in South Korea by practicing participatory observation with three groups of the surveyors. Although Aryn Martin and Micheal Lynch greatly contributed to understandings of practice of counting in STS terms (Martin and Lynch, 2009) it is a type of numeration involving in pre-processing of making counting objects docile enough to be counted. What if we shed light on the practice of counting of wild animals which one must not be interfering or even touching with? In this paper, I attempted to outline an alternative reading of counting practice in terms of co-construction in the more balanced language between humans and nonhuman nature with the aid of recent studies of STS which had explored the distinct features of field science and the companion-like relationships between humans and animals. In particular, I argue that the census surveyors have "response-ability," following Haraway's description of people and their companion dogs (Haraway, 2008): however, it is applied in a disparate context. The surveyors in the Winter Waterbird Census are not allowed to actively interfere with wild birds to facilitate enumeration. It is both an ability and a responsibility to enumerate proficiently without requiring the wild birds to respond to human practices in any situation. I have listed three

"responses-abilities." The census surveyors must have site knowledge, rapid bird identification, and accurate bird counts, which take time to develop. I show that slowly acquired skills of the Winter Waterbird Census is broadening our understanding of numeration practices on wild animals.

Feminist Crops: A More-Than-Human Concept for Advancing Feminist Crop Breeding for Development *Ida Tarjem*, NMBU Noragric

In recognizing that "gender matters" in agriculture, crop breeding teams are increasingly being asked to develop plant varieties that respond to the needs and preferences of both men and women. However, achieving gender-responsive crop breeding requires communication and cooperation across disciplines, not least between crop breeders and gender specialists. The coming together of plant sciences and gender studies necessitates novel ethico-onto-epistemological ideas, concepts, and approaches that unite nature with culture and the material with the social. However, the development of such approaches is still in its infancy. Empirically grounded in personal experiences in and ethnographic observations of social and natural scientists working at the intersection of gender and crop breeding in an African context, this largely theoretical paper contributes to filling this void by proposing the concept of the "feminist crop". The feminist crop builds on a naturecultural and sociomaterial ontology and a more-than-human, more-than-social, and distributive notion of agency and represents an ethically embedded and fertile meeting ground between plant sciences and gender studies. Using examples from banana, yam, and cassava, I explore how the feminist crop can expand on both the natural and social sciences of crop breeding and extend what becomes possible for feminist crop breeding for development.

Pasturing Cheese: Challenging Dairy Infrastructures in Northeastern Turkey *Mehmet Fatih Tatari*, University of California, Davis (UCD)

This article investigates infrastructures of dairy farming and artisanal cheesemaking in rural Kars, Northeastern Turkey. Following my 18-month ethnographic research on dairy farming and dairy sciences in this borderland, I conceptualize dairy infrastructures as the assemblage of socio-technical practices of obtaining milk in pastures and crafting it into cheeses. National food safety regulations - and the underlying scientific knowledge - prioritize industrial dairy infrastructures at the expense of "traditional," "inefficient" and "unsafe/not hygienic" production in pastures. I focus on an unlikely collaboration between scientists and small dairy farmers, which has altered dairy infrastructures in rural Kars in the last ten years through practices of what I call "pasturing cheese." While most scientific studies failed to engineer the distinctive microbiological composition of pasture-cheeses into starter cultures for dairy industry, their failures gave rise to new questions on the responsibility of various actors in the dairy infrastructures and on the socio-ecological resilience in pastures. By analyzing how pastures emerge in the cheese that is crafted in rural dairies by farmers, and analyzed in laboratories by scientists, I suggest that the innovative techno-scientific processes result from this collaboration and challenge ecologically destructive dairy infrastructures.

Session Organizer:

Allison Marie Loconto, INRAE

446. Artificial Intelligence in Health and Care: Development, Governance, and Ethics

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Discourses around the future potential and imagined impacts of AI are reaching new heights of aspiration globally. In particular, Japan - with the world's most rapidly ageing society - published a major national AI Strategy in 2019. The document is imbued with a rhetoric of AI 'saving' the country from current and future societal crises that has long

characterised national policy around techno-science (Šabanović 2014; Frumer 2018; Robertson 2018; Wright 2019). Similar rhetoric is also found in South Korea, China, Singapore, and Taiwan, which have published a flurry of national AI strategy documents since 2017. This panel critically examines how AI and related technologies such as socially assistive robots and the internet of things are imagined or expected to transform futures of health and social care in these countries, and how key actors in the government, industry, and third sector propose that they be governed. Focusing on cases from East Asia, we invite a critical discussion drawing on the following questions: - What forms of AI and related technologies, such as robotics, are actually being developed and deployed in health and care? - How does the aspirational rhetoric of AI connect with realities of use? - How are the ethics and governance of AI systems being conceptualised, drawn up into guidelines and principles, and operationalised? - Where is the “human” in “human-centric AI”? The panel will consist of 5 presentations lasting 15 minutes each, as well as a comment from the discussant and 40 minutes of questions and discussion.

Participants:

“Total globalization”?: Exploring the development of Japan’s AI governance and ethics landscape. *James Wright, The Alan Turing Institute; David Leslie, The Alan Turing Institute*

Over the past decade, the Japanese government has released a series of guidelines and policy documents setting out positions on the ethics and governance of AI, culminating in the 2019 publication of the “Social Principles of Human-Centric AI” and a new national AI Strategy. Amid the recent global scramble to develop AI governance and ethics frameworks, Japan has sought a leadership role, brokering broad consensus on basic ethical principles at the OECD and G7. A central element of the documents is their presentation of AI as both a product and an agent of radical societal transformation. While AI is expected to transform society, society must first be transformed to prepare the ground for AI, in order to achieve a pluralist, internationalist, and utopian “Society 5.0” in which “national borders, industries, academia, governments, race, gender, nationality, age, political convictions and religion” are transcended, in order to achieve “total globalization” (Social Principles 2019). This paper examines the development of the Japanese government’s approach to AI governance and ethics, based on analysis of key documents and semi-structured interviews with several of the architects of Japan’s AI policies who helped write them. It explores how and to what extent the techno-futurist rhetoric of internationalism and radical societal transformation contained in the documents connects with the Japanese government’s wider conservative yet technocratic vision (Robertson 2018), considers what socio-technical imaginaries (Jasanoff and Kim 2015) are being constructed, and examines how firmly grounded they are in the reality of development communities and practices in Japan.

Machines Caring For Us? Technoscientific Imaginaries and Practical Uses of Socially Assistive Robotics *Giulia De Togni, University of Edinburgh*

This paper interrogates the narratives produced by engineers, data scientists and practitioners in relation to the societal impact and levels of acceptability of ‘Socially Assistive Robots’ (SARs) for the healthcare sector. It is based on 30 interviews collected in 2020 with stakeholders based in the UK, Europe, USA, Australia, and New Zealand. It analyses the stakeholders’ “technoscientific imaginaries” (Marcus 1995), namely how they envisioned future promise, potential and challenges of using these technologies. It is also informed by media analysis of 50 articles from 6 major UK newspapers which focus on public expectations towards and imaginaries of social robots. The paper problematises how a rhetoric of urgency concerning ageing populations globally has driven the development of SARs - a technological fix to a social problem - and how such rhetoric has remained focused merely on how society can adapt to these technologies. Jasanoff’s (2015) concept of “sociotechnical imaginaries” is used to contextualise

these discourses in the wider debate of how society should instead actively shape new technologies. Taking as case study ‘super ageing’ Japan, the country currently leading globally in the production of SARs, the paper calls for the need to co-design and co-produce these technologies with the final users. Finally, it offers practical suggestions on how to redefine a framework for evaluating SARs based on an interdisciplinary expertise from a range of disciplines, stressing in particular what contribution social sciences can make to this timely research.

Closing the Care Gap: Robot and AI Services for Elderly Care in South Korea *Chihyung Jeon, KAIST; Heesun Shin, KAIST (Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology)*

In this paper, we examine two kinds of robot and AI elderly care services operating in South Korea: the Hyodol and the AI Social Worker. Hyodol is a personal toy-robot developed for the elderly living alone. By offering various healthcare and entertainment services, Hyodol is expected to serve as a companion for the elderly who are supposedly lonely and depressed. Since its release in 2017, more than 2,000 units of Hyodol have been distributed to individual homes of the elderly nationwide. The other elderly care technology is the AI Social Worker developed by KT Corporation, South Korea’s largest telecommunications company. Operating as a voice-bot system, the AI Social Worker makes calls to over 8,000 older adults and asks questions about their physical and mental health conditions. The older adults’ spoken responses are automatically converted to texts, stored, and transmitted to human social workers. Behind the rise of robotic and AI care in South Korea lies a growing concern over workforce shortage in the aging society, which results in the “care gap” in elderly care. With the ongoing COVID-19 pandemic, robots and AI have gained momentum as a provider of contact-free care. The aspirational rhetoric of “care gap” contributes to the development and use of the robots and AI, which are expected to fill the gap where humans are in shortage. By comparing the use of Hyodol and AI Social Worker, we ask how the new technological measures reconfigure the public elderly care system as well as the concept of care.

Conceptualizing Robotic Agency: Social Robots in Elder Care in Contemporary Japan *Anne Stefanie Aronsson, University of Zurich*

Japan is a hyper-aging society with one of the highest life expectancies in the world and is undergoing demographic transitions Western nations have yet to experience. The Japanese government is encouraging robotic solutions to address its elder care labor shortage, and authorities have therefore adopted an agenda of introducing social robots. However, increasing numbers of people in Japan are becoming emotionally attached to anthropomorphic machines, and their introduction into elder care may thus be perceived as contentious. By exploring human engagement with social robots in the care context, this presentation argues that rapid technological advances in the twenty-first century will see robots achieve some level of agency, contributing to human society by carving out unique roles for themselves and by bonding with humans. Nevertheless, the questions remain of whether there should be a difference between humans attributing agency to a being and those beings having the inherent ability to produce agency and how we might understand that difference if unable to access the minds of other humans, let alone nonhumans, some of which are not even alive in the classical sense. Using the example of an interaction between an elderly woman and a social robot, I engage with these questions; discuss linguistic, attributed, and inherent agencies; and suggest that a processual type of agency might be most appropriate for understanding human–robot interaction. As we start to treat machines as if they are almost human, we may begin to develop habits that cause us to treat humans as almost machines.

Artificial Intelligence, Robots and Dementia: An Exploration of

Human(ness) and Techno-centrism in the Usage of Medical Robots in South Korea *Seonsam Na, Kuri Hanbit Convalescent Hospital; Eunjeong Ma, Pohang University of Science and Technology*

Scientific technology has always been central in biomedicine and with the ascent of AI/robotics technology, their clinical use is increasing. In South Korea, IBM Watson and surgical robots are actively applied and the robots aiding rehabilitation are being trialed. Some of the industry-wide factors behind this increased medical application of robotic technology can be found in the country's political economy: as a newly developed economy, it needs industrial deepening in high value-added sectors such as robotics and pharmaceuticals, and the government has heavily invested in them. The changed portfolio of the chaebols' business operations reflects this macro-economic trend. This paper aims to provide an overview of the usage of AI/robotic medical technology in South Korea, and investigate its clinical and sociopolitical implications. In doing so, it seeks to explore the changed conceptions of human(ness) encountered in the interface between AI/robotics and the human cum social body, and the nature of techno-centric tendencies manifested in these endeavors. These tendencies will be contextualized within the societal attitude toward technology in general or AI/robotics in particular, i.e. in comparison with 'techno-nationalism' observed in Japanese robotics (Robertson 2018). Empirical data will be obtained from doctors and developers who are able to offer insights into their value. Insights from those working with people suffering from dementia are given particular emphasis as – considering the quest of AI/robotics to produce 'human-like' cognition – their understandings of cognitive impairment will provide a useful platform on which to interrogate the fundamental underpinnings of the field's development in medicine.

Session Organizer:

Giulia De Togni, University of Edinburgh

Chair:

James Wright, The Alan Turing Institute

Discussant:

Yulia Frumer, Johns Hopkins University

447. Democracy, (In)Security, and Technology - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

Participants:

Beyond mistrust: legitimacy, authority and contestation in the official profiles of the Brazilian government *Thaiane de oliveira*

The context of the health crisis in Brazil is also crossed by a political and epistemic crisis, in which trust in the basic institutions of modernity has been gradually imploded. This crisis lead to the presidency Jair Messias Bolsonaro, whose built his political agenda under the discourse of distrust in epistemic institutions. Currently, the government has been active not only in delegitimizing scientific research, but also in legitimizing controversial scientific research or in initial stages. The purpose of this work is to present the discursive strategies used by governmental profiles that act in the delegitimation of epistemic authority. Using the CrowdTangle tool, we conducted a content analysis on 217 posts from three Facebook. The results show that: 1) The official presidential profile forces the frontiers of legitimacy of scientific authority in their speeches. He uses the ill-defined sense of disinformation when claiming to suffer attacks from "fake news" or "disinformation" by his opponents. 2) The official government channel, presents statistical data reinforcing the idea of neutrality and refer to the government's own communication secretariat as an informational authority. 3) The communication secretariat channel encourages criticism and

contestation as democratic rights, emphasizing how important media and information literacy actions are important for this. Without a clear definition of what disinformation is, the term has been disputed in different spheres, as an epistemological war (boyd, 2017) in which serves as a political strategy of legitimizing the own communication channels as epistemic authority and as a way to delegitimize their opponents.

Brains, Bots, and Blinding Lasers: Object Metaphors and the 'Preemptive' Regulation of LAWS *Michael Bivona, Georgia Institute of Technology*

Since 2014, state parties to the United Nations Convention on Certain Conventional Weapons (CCW) have been engaged in a lively public debate over the science, ethics, and politics of Lethal Autonomous Weapons Systems (LAWS) – a technology that arguably does not and may never exist. Drawing on position papers and other relevant artifacts, this paper examines the construction and deployment of object metaphors, through which participants ground claims about what LAWS can, will, or should not do. The main sections track three main groups: technological/scientific metaphors (i.e. LAWS are Cybernetic), ethical metaphors (i.e. LAWS are Armed Drones), and legal metaphors (i.e. LAWS are 'blinding lasers'). Each helps illuminate connections between otherwise disparate polities, creating a surprisingly vibrant, multi-polar debate. Indeed, despite the CCW's well-documented structural inequities, large, powerful nations remain fully engaged. There is also little evidence to suggest that global opinion is warming to the notion of unmanned weaponry, despite assurances from its staunchest promoters. But this focus on metaphor also seems to displace serious engagement with the history of battlefield automation. A host of underlying assumptions (i.e. that automation will be cheaper, less politically risky, etc.) that go largely unchallenged, and developments in fields like Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning, and Robotics, are not situated in relation to other, earlier attempts. This makes it difficult to say what, if anything, has changed, and how its further development might impact people outside the lab.

Cybersecurity and the Politics of Extremism *Jeffrey Whyte, Newton International Postdoctoral Fellow, Politics, University of Manchester*

Since 2016, questions concerning disinformation, fake news, and the so-called 'post-truth' era have suffused discussions of foreign policy and national security. Where cybersecurity once denoted the protection of computer networks and critical digital infrastructures, its scope now broadens to include questions of digitally mediated political communication. As the US foreign policy establishment pivots to 'defend democracy' against these digital threats, little attention has been paid to the way in which this new cybersecurity paradigm has altered the domestic US political landscape. Drawing on case studies of the Black Lives Matter (BLM) movement and the Jan 6, 2021 Capitol Hill riot in Washington, DC, this paper considers how the new logic of cybersecurity has combined with recent concerns over the problem of domestic political extremism. I argue that this combination has framed the political protest as a vehicle for, and product of, foreign cyberwarfare aimed at destabilizing domestic political order. In both cases this process of cybersecuritization has been deeply racialized, with both Black activists and white supremacists standing accused of destabilizing US democracy through the production of 'racial tension'. I consider how this flattened vision of 'racial tension' has produced a false equivalence between racists and anti-racists under the umbrella of 'political extremism' in a way that seeks to frame Black activism as an 'excess of democracy' whose political horizons require foreclosure in the name of national security.

Liberty and Death: Paranoia and Resistance to Public Health Measures in the Era of COVID-19 *Steven Tran-Creque, CUNY Graduate Center*

While countries with prior experience with SARS and MERS have generally responded to COVID-19 with robust quarantine and contact tracing measures, the American response has been comparatively patchwork, incoherent, politicized, and often dramatically contested. Relatively mild public health orders have provoked and unified significant popular resistance and resentment, and a confluence of QAnon believers, libertarians, gun rights activists, anti-vaxxers, “boogaloo bois” and many others have staged spectacular armed protests against policies and politicians they see as unconstitutional and tyrannical. Why have these groups reacted so militantly to what scientists and academics generally view as apolitical and mild public health interventions? What should social scientists make of broadly popular radical libertarian critiques of the biopolitical state in a state of emergency? Why has scientific knowledge been popularly rendered as utterly incredible across these groups? What are the consequences of a state response that demands people stay home while providing only the most threadbare forms of support? And how should social scientists assess the popular insurrectionary rhetoric of revolution and civil war one finds in these protests following the US Capitol siege? Drawing on extensive ethnographic research in the gun rights movement, this paper explores the peculiarly American constitutional rights discourse and conspiratorial reactions to biopolitical public health interventions, placing them in the context of a resurgent global right populist movement, in order to make sense of populist right’s perspectives with particular attention to how this bears on sites of extreme social inequality, race formation, and scientific knowledge claims.

Making Arms Control: How knowledge and expertise shape arms control negotiations of emerging weapons technologies

Anna-Katharina Ferl, Peace Research Institute Frankfurt

Technologies and international politics have an intimate relationship. Technological innovation pervades almost every aspect of international relations. It has been a constant catalyst for military success, security and the shifting balance of power among states. Yet, theories of International Relations (IR) have only started to adequately account for the technological artefacts in global politics. One of the most prominently discussed emerging technologies in IR today takes place in the area of Artificial Intelligence (AI). This is especially true for the potential of weaponisation of AI in the shape of lethal autonomous weapon systems (LAWS). While the consequences of these technologies of global politics remain yet to be determined, attempts to regulate, prohibit or otherwise contain the destructiveness of weapons political processes of arms control are already taking place. Arms control negotiations are an interesting avenue for the analysis of controversies within, and intersections between, technological developments, socio-political processes, and knowledge about security. The integration of Science and Technology Studies (STS) into the theoretical and empirical analysis of arms control processes promises new perspectives in overcoming shortcomings of tradition IR theories. This paper presents a theoretical framework drawing on the insights of STS to understand how arms control negotiation processes produce knowledge; as well as the ways in which artefacts ‘make’ arms control politics. A STS perspective provides political science and arms control research with a meaningful toolbox to study emerging weapons technologies that are based on AI, in their constitution within a particular context.

Session Organizer:

Scott Timcke

448. Performativity and Pragmatics in Water Governance - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Water governance is one of the critical challenges facing communities, regions, and states around the world in the twenty-first century. Water related crises and inequities, due to their urgency and centrality to

existence, call for a pragmatic orientation that can mask the performative nature of pragmatic doing. Science, feminist scholars and queer theorists point out, is both situated and enacted. The idea of performativity, in its many definitions, has been applied across diverse disciplines, including a performative turn in Science and Technology Studies. Recognizing current relations as constructed or performed opens new lines of inquiry into the pragmatics of water governance and water justice. Building on Ballesteros’s (2019) insight that technological, material, and legal devices are central to current practices of water governance, as well as to efforts for new forms of governance, we invite papers that engage with the performativity of doing, demonstrating, and/or disciplining (Kirshenblatt-Gimblett 1999) the sociomateriality of the hydrosocial system. What can thinking with performativity contribute to conversations around water justice and water governance? Similarly, in what ways does doing performativity create potential (or not) for enacting different relations of care and/or harm? We are especially interested in bringing together diverse perspectives from scholars, practitioners, activists, and artists. Attending to the practices of water-related (broadly conceived) science and governance, and the ways watery relations exceed these frames, these conversations may consider (but are not limited to): methods, boundaries, relations, flows, effects, materialities, geographies, temporalities, devices, and socio-technical assemblages.

Participants:

Seeking Clarity *alexandra lakind, University of Wisconsin-Madison; Rob Lundberg, Independent Artist*

We have embarked on a photographic practice documenting water and sewer line covers—circles that hint at vast systems. Our presentation will share multiple media—photographs, graphic scores, musical recordings, text—inspired by this act of stopping and looking. We aim to invite attendees into a messy, fluid world that curb stops attempt to regulate and simplify. This artistic practice is part of an ongoing curiosity around the linkages between water and U.S. property systems. Property is meant to clarify rights to a piece of land or quantity of water. Yet, clearly bounding place is akin to dreams of pure and clear water – both aspirational fictions of fixing the unstable. In a forthcoming chapter on the infrastructures of art/scholarship (Lakind, Bennett, Lundberg, 2021), we adopted Thompson’s (2015) concept of “infrastructures of resonance,” the material conditions surrounding a given artist or project, to think through relations that shift attention to systems that produce meaning. By looking downward to these cast iron circles, we can consider: the presence (or absence) of water infrastructure, its state of (dis)repair, and the settler propertied logics that undergird pipes, covers, treatment plants. Water pipes seek to settle divisions between private and public manifesting settler colonial governance. Property is not static but requires active doing (Blomley, 2004). Likewise, water is adept at dissolving and carrying substances. Water mingles. Water resists property’s constraints. Meanwhile pipes work to shelter potable water from contamination and shepherd sewage away, separating desirables from undesirables. Clarity is sought on all fronts.

On the Enaction of Absence: Water Quality Data Gaps and Regulatory Redaction *Kallista Bley, University of Wisconsin-Madison*

Drinking water quality and the limitations of monitoring and regulation are ongoing issues of community concern in the central valleys of California. The extent and frequency of water quality testing varies for example across water system types—whether public water systems, small water systems (state or local), or domestic wells—and across toxic substances, many of which remain unmonitored. Attending to the material practices of this testing involves consideration of what is not monitored, as much as to those practices implemented and present (e.g., specific sampling approaches, locations, quantifications). Extending the work of feminist geographic scholarship on voids and science and technology (STS) perspectives on measurement, I consider data gaps and regulatory redactions related to drinking

water quality testing through examples such as domestic well water exclusions and shifting hexavalent chromium (CrVI) regulations. I argue that what is enacted through these absences and exclusions—alongside how these monitoring exclusions are contested—shape pragmatic efforts at accountability and uneven geographies of risk.

Performing collaboration in water resource management *Noel Vineyard, Portland State University; Alida Cantor, Portland State University*

Collaborative natural resource governance is often touted as a model for generating “win-win” management decisions that are amenable to all stakeholders in a place. However, stakeholders are seldom all able to collaborate from equal positions of power. This research explores the question: what happens in collaborative water governance when the principal stakeholders hold all the water rights and oppose change? In Oregon’s Deschutes Basin, numerous collaborative efforts have been undertaken to establish new environmentally conscious water governance regimes, however progress has been stymied by the Basin’s irrigation districts who hold rights to the majority of the Deschutes River’s apportionable flows. In a series of interviews conducted with water governance collaborative participants, a concern emerged that, through a seemingly revolving series of collaborative efforts, the irrigation districts were “performing collaboration” as a means of greenwashing their water management practices that are environmentally destructive to the habitat of many of the Basin’s endangered species. By holding the rights to the Deschutes River’s water, but also by serving as the party determining collaboration participants, the districts may lack incentive to engage in functioning collaboration. They may rather seek to perform collaboration to further cultivate social capital among a broader stakeholder base. This work examines the ways in which existing legal structures governing water resources in the American West may create instances of post-political performances of water governance that may not, in practice, serve all of the stakeholder interests they purport to serve.

Transboundary Salmon Governance: A Kin-study of Perception, Refusal, and Care across the Salish Sea *Izzi Lavallee, University of Washington*

Water refuses colonial notions of borders, as do many peoples and other-than human individuals within waterways. The borders between the United States and Canadian nation-states reify, perform and reproduce settler-identities (Simpson, 2014; Walia, 2013). Established by settler nation-states in the 1800s, the 49th parallel cuts through the Salish Sea, a transboundary waterway situated within Coast Salish territories. My qualitative research reveals Coast Salish perceptions on the invisible 49th parallel, which my interlocutors call “fictitious,” “frustrating,” and divisive towards “identity and mobility”. In addition, I examine the resurgence of indigenous-lead performance around the ‘Trans Mountain Pipeline expansion’, ‘Canoe Journey revitalization’ and movements such as ‘Missing & Murdered Indigenous Relatives No Borders!’. These movements suggest a praxis of abolition ecologies and decolonization across the 49th parallel, building upon theories put forth by scholars Ybarra (2020) and Yazzie (2020). These politics of refusal perform new lines of inquiry that encourage transformative thinking towards kin-ship with the water, which moves freely beyond borders. Lastly, I employ qualitative methods to discern perceptions on current ecosystem management measures performed throughout the Salish Sea, especially locating spaces of harm towards Coast Salish Salmon Peoples. I explore the impact of climate change which necessitates new formations of care-based governance within the transboundary watershed, in order to expand adaptive capacity and indigenous self-determination. I ask the audience: how might we think with the water and those who have ancestral relationships to this waterway, as we theorize new notions of water governance?

Session Organizers:

Kallista Bley, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Marisa Manheim

Christy Spackman, SFIS - Arizona State University

Chair:

Christy Spackman, SFIS - Arizona State University

Discussant:

Andrea Ballestero, University of Southern California

449. Innovative biotechnologies, co-regulation and bionetworking

I: Mapping innovation arenas

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Repeatedly, when medical scientists propose the authorization of new biotechnologies, fears and hopes emerge alongside new impasses, legal frictions, and uncertainties. This applies, for example, to cutting-edge therapies potentially capable of treating chronic diseases and, hence, of substituting pharmaceuticals that are currently in use (sometimes paradigmatically). While navigating between this skepticism towards regulatory authorities and reassurances of faith in science, which biopolitical agendas are enacted and disseminated by the proposed biotechnologies in contemporary health innovation arenas? This panel aims to explore the impacts of new health technologies on different societies and how, in turn, multiple actors affect them, including their evaluation processes, design and related policies. The panel invites contributions that address aspects of the development, circulation, and co-regulation of novel biotechnologies as relatable to forms of bionetworking (e.g. judicialization, biohacking, infrastructuring, co-production of expertise and digital activism). Bionetworking practices comprise collaborative relationships between scientists, patients, their caretakers, and other actors (including biological, legal, and entrepreneurial ones), to support and/or disqualify promising biotechnologies. In light of this, the panel provides a platform to discuss the actuality of concepts linked to the STS-field of biocitizenship like political economies of hope, life assemblages, adoption space, among others. It looks to discuss controversies in areas such as vaccinology, regenerative medicine, gene therapy, translational and precision medicine, microbiome-based therapies, and experimental therapies more broadly. A central point of reflection concerns how tensions between different ways of assessing the efficacy and innovativeness of proposed biotechnologies, and of co-producing medical evidence, might become co-constitutive of biosocialities.

Participants:

Determining the key actors and contents of the prevailing biomedical research agenda *Mercedes Garcia Carrillo, Instituto de Biociencias, Biotecnología y Biología traslacional (iB3), Universidad de Buenos Aires; Testoni Federico, Instituto de Lingüística, Facultad de Filosofía y Letras, Universidad de Buenos Aires, Argentina; Marc-Andre Gagnon, School of Public Policy and Administration, Carleton University, Canada; Cecilia Rikap, Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET). Centre Population et Développement; Matías Blaustein, Consejo Nacional de Investigaciones Científicas y Técnicas (CONICET)- Instituto de Biociencias, Biot*

Conflicts of interest in biomedical research can influence research results and drive research agendas away from what is most relevant to public health. Previous agenda-setting studies share two shortfalls, they only account for direct connections between institutions and private firms and a potential bias based on researchers’ personal beliefs. The goal of this investigation was to determine the key actors and contents of the prevailing health and biomedical sciences (HBMS) research agenda. In order to do so, we performed a bibliometric and lexical analysis of 95,415 scientific articles published between 1999 and 2018 in the highest impact factor journals within HBMS, using the Web of Science database and the CorText platform. HBMS’s

prevailing knowledge network of institutions was proxied with network maps where nodes represent affiliations and edges the most frequent co-authorships. The content of the prevailing HBMS research agenda was depicted through co-occurrence network maps of prevalent multi-terms found in titles, keywords, and abstracts. Our results show that large private firms' and leading academic institutions' HBMS research agendas are intertwined. The prevailing HBMS agenda is mostly based on molecular biology, with an inclination towards cancer and cardiovascular research. Studies on pathogens and biological vectors related to recent epidemics are marginal. The content of the prevailing HBMS research agenda prioritizes research on pharmacological intervention over research on socio-environmental factors influencing disease onset or progression and overlooks, among others, the study of infectious diseases. We conclude that a more balanced HBMS research agenda, together with epistemological approaches that consider socio-environmental factors associated with disease spreading, could contribute to being better prepared to prevent and treat more diverse pathologies and to improve overall health outcomes.

Reflection of the Fundamental Principles of Human Genome Research in Japan *Jusaku Minari, Kyoto University; Kayo Takashima, Kyoto University*

Genome-wide sequencing technologies currently contribute to the understanding and application of individual genomic information in medical research and care. Some key social benefits using these technologies can be seen in newly developed diagnoses and treatments. Although these scientific progressions are highly expected for the future, there are potential ethical and legal ramifications. In particular, the frameworks of genome research are increasingly questioned because genome-related data and samples are deeply associated with each person. Japan has two ethical regulations governing human genome research. These are the Fundamental Principles of Research on the Human Genome (Fundamental Principles) set by the Bioethics Committee of the Council for Science and Technology in 2000 and the Ethical Guidelines for Human Genome/Gene Analysis Research set by three ministries in 2001. While the latter presents concrete procedures and standards for informed consent and research ethics committees, the former shows basic concepts regarding the human genome and its related research. This study explores historical implications of the Fundamental Principles, their relationships with specific ethical guidelines, and the consideration of scientific and social changes. Given the recent trends in the European Union and Japan to govern human genome data as personal data, the study can be useful in reconsidering the value of the human genome and in developing further debates regarding relevant regulations in international contexts.

When Crowds Judge Science: Citizens' Evaluations of Project Social Impact *Chiara Franzoni, Politecnico di Milano; Henry Sauermann, ESMT Berlin; Diletta Di Marco, Politecnico di Milano*

There have long been concerns that the professional scientific system puts too little weight on the social benefits (and costs) of research when setting research agendas. To address this problem, novel approaches allow individual citizens to directly influence research agendas by voting on research proposals or by funding research projects with their own money. Although there is a hope that such mechanisms can help "democratize" science and increase societal relevance, it is not clear how citizens evaluate the potential social impact of research projects. We asked over 2,000 citizens to evaluate funding proposals written for the general public in the social, natural, and medical sciences. We elicited assessments of different project attributes (e.g., scientific merit, researcher capabilities, social impact), recommendations for funding, as well as real donations using personal money. Using these data, we first confirm the common assumption that

citizens put a high weight on social impact when evaluating research projects. We then analyze how judgments of social impact relate to individual-level attributes such as level of education, income, and personal relevance of the project topic. Qualitative data provide additional insights into what exactly people think about when judging projects' social impact. Our study contributes to the literature in STS by examining how novel participatory mechanisms can allow citizens to shape research agendas and the progress of science. We also contribute to the broader literature on science and innovation management as well as crowdsourcing. Our results have practical implications for professional scientists, funding agencies, and policymakers.

Session Organizer:

Márcio Vilar, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany

Discussant:

Carlos Novas, Carleton University

450. The Biomedicalization of Social Medicine? - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Biomedicalization scholars have argued that studies of biomedicalization need to be situated in their geopolitical context and within that context's history of approaches to health and healing (Clarke et al 2010). Biomedicalization can be absent in some sites, or it can be contested by a diverse set of other approaches to healing (such as non-Western practices of medicine). Yet such contestations within the field of medicine itself have often been overlooked in the literature on biomedicalization. One such field is social medicine, a field concerned with the social determinants of health and the relations of medicine and social justice. In this panel, we trace the blurred and contested boundaries between social medicine and biomedicalization. Some practices of social medicine have included at the same time social forms of care and biomedicalized approaches. Other social medicine practices have explicitly challenged biomedicalization processes. At different times and places, proponents of social medicine have argued that it has been too much biomedicine (at the expense of social, political and legal approaches), or that it has been too little of it (HIV treatment in low income countries, access to gender-affirming therapy). Sometimes, biomedicalization processes initially promoted by social medicine in the name of solidarity or health equity, have been transformed into more techno-science-dependent forms of practice, sometimes in stratified forms. In this open panel, we aim to explore diverse empirical examples of interdependencies, interconnectedness and contestations between biomedicine and social medicine in different historical and contemporary sites.

Participants:

Between social medicine and biomedicalization: the emergence of lifestyle risk *Mikko Jauho, University of Helsinki*

We are living under conditions of 'mass health' (Dumit 2012): the increasing treatment of risk populations instead of singular individuals with illness. Today, medicine addresses not only presently felt symptoms or signs of actual disease, but also test-induced risk markers of a possible future condition. This paper discusses the rise of this risk factor approach in public health, encapsulated by the notion of lifestyle risk. Common chronic diseases, such as cardiovascular diseases and diabetes, which dominate statistics in the industrialized West and increasingly in the Global South, have been connected to mundane everyday habits, such as diet and exercising. Consequently, the onus of preventive efforts has been placed on individuals, who are expected to take care of their health in a responsible manner. However, as has been previously argued (Berridge 2007; Porter 2011), this prime example of biomedicalization, often associated with the wider process of neoliberalization, was in fact facilitated by more 'social' aspirations, prevalent in the building period of modern welfare states. This paper tracks the role of social medicine in the establishment of lifestyle risk and the gradual biomedicalization of the approach. As the empirical point of entry, it uses coronary heart disease (CHD) in post-WW2

Finland. The case is salient, since Finland was for many decades at the top of international CHD mortality statistics for middle-aged males, the prime risk group, as well as the site for important international epidemiological and preventive studies promoting the risk factor approach and lifestyle risk.

Biofeminism: Sex, science, and the pursuit of gender equity
Madeleine Pape, Northwestern University

In this presentation, I develop an account of biofeminism: A political formation that seeks to root gender equity and women's inclusion in a binary model of biological difference through the pursuit of the latter as an object of scientific knowledge and regulation. At the core of biofeminism is a commitment to the scientific pursuit of "biological sex" as a worthy end in of itself, one can be put to work in service of women and which is believed to be a fundamental condition of their inclusion in certain arenas. Yet with what consequences—and at what cost—for the realization of gender equity? I examine two institutional domains where biofeminist activity has succeeded in shaping policies for women's inclusion and embedding a certain understanding of "sex" in regulation: international sport, and biomedical research in the United States (U.S.). In the former, the regulation of female athlete eligibility has attracted considerable scientific and human rights critiques in recent years. In the latter, the National Institutes of Health (NIH) has mandated consideration of sex as a "biological variable" in all basic and preclinical research, with far less institutional investment in pursuing gender as a social health determinant. In both cases, feminists have been divided over whether and how scientific notions of sex can and should be put to work in service of gender equity. I identify several key ontological, epistemic, and political dimensions of biofeminism: its commitment to the uniqueness of "sex" as a purportedly universal form of binary variation; the attempted anti-intersectional divorcing of "sex" from the complexities of gender, race, and nation that follows from this claim to universality; and the wielding of "sex" as justification not only for inclusion but also exclusion, as the case of sport so aptly demonstrates.

Framing Drug Use Among Youth: The Norwegian Medico-Legal Conceptualization Of A 'Drug Epidemic' (1965–1976)
Per Haave, Institute of health and society, University of Oslo

This paper analyses the conceptualization of the emerging drug taking among youth in Norway from the late 1960s as an epidemic occurrence of use. It is argued that the concept of 'drug epidemic', as applied in the Norwegian setting, originated in a social medical approach to drug dependency and conflated with the criminal law idea of punishment as general and individual prevention. Further, the paper argues that this concerted medico-legal approach became instrumental in the shaping of a restrictive drug policy, which in 1968 extended the ban of drugs from possession to taking and increased the punishment for professional drug criminals, both in order to stem the advance of an alleged menace that infected society. However, the paper reveals that the 'drug epidemic' was a contested concept. Within medicine itself, the concept provoked a tension between a social medical perception of addiction as a multifaceted symptom and a biomedical perception of addiction as a disease in biological terms. Outside medicine, social scientists questioned the scientific, political and moral relevance of the concept. This caused, I will argue, an attempt by the Norwegian health authorities to introduce a more complex, social medical concept of 'drug epidemic', however, without letting go the punitive drug laws created within the context of the original notion of 'drug epidemic'. I draw on archival material, medical publications, newspapers and parliamentary papers to demonstrate how and why the contested and shifting concept of 'drug epidemic' came to inform the Norwegian drug policy in its formative years.

Moving health research upstream: mapping perceptions on priorities in cardiovascular research
Wouter Van de Klippe;

Ismael Rafols, Centre for Science & Technology Studies (CWTS), Leiden University

Public health literature has long argued for the need to shift priorities towards the upstream determinants of health. There exist compelling arguments for this shift based on general reductions of disease burden, reductions of health inequality and economic efficiency in terms of the return on the investment towards upstream determinants. These arguments, originating in discussions on the need for public health expenditure to move upstream have been extended to expenditures in research on health as well. This gap, between the knowledge that is perceived as needed, and the current distribution of research priorities, is what we seek to explore within this project. In this study, we inquire into the perceptions of researchers and research managers regarding current and desirable priorities on cardiovascular research in western Europe. Three main findings stand out from the interviews. First, understandings and ontologies of the fields constituting cardiovascular research are extremely disparate and highly dependent on the disciplinary and professional background of the experts. Second, there is consensus that research priorities should be more evenly spread across different fields in particular towards upstream research. Third, while most experts acknowledge that research should move towards social medicine, this is generally limited to reducing individual risk factors and improving lifestyles, rather than broader socio-environmental determinants. The interviews also portrayed major disconnections between social medicine, biomedical research and clinical practice.

Social Medicine and Epidemiology in Sweden, 1950s to 2010s
Ida Al Fakir, Stockholm University

My paper discusses socio-medical and epidemiological knowledge production concerning ethnicity and minorities in Sweden from the 1950s to the 2010s. The aim is to shed light on how processes of biomedicalization (Clarke et al 2011) have evolved, or indeed been challenged, in a Swedish context. Porter (2011) describes how modern epidemiology after WWII established links between inequality and disease causation, which worked to supply the new discipline of social medicine with scientific authority. In Sweden, social medicine became a key area in the formation of social questions in the post-war decades. Conditions previously described as lacks or disorders leading to exclusion were reassessed and new possibilities for inclusion opened up. Social medicine provided the ideological and theoretical foundations and the practical tools for the elimination of unwanted situations and rehabilitation of problematic groups (e.g. ethnic minorities) to normality. The influence of social medicine in this respect waned, however, towards the end of the 1970s. In the early 1980s, the Swedish Medical Research Council identified epidemiology as a strategic research area. The paper will discuss whether the expansion of epidemiology, while still searching for the social determinants of health but distancing itself from the justice-and-rights-discourse central to post-war social medicine, may be analysed in terms of a de-politicization of social medicine. Placing the development within the framework of biomedicalization, the paper elaborates on these processes and the possible contestations, interconnections and/or interdependencies that characterized them.

Session Organizer:

Jeremy A Greene, Johns Hopkins University

Chair:

Anne Lie

Discussant:

Carlo Caduff

451. Understanding Gene Technology in Terms of Relationality: A Move Toward More Constructive Deliberations?

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

For three decades now, social science and humanities scholars have pointed out how public debates on gene technology are hampered by the strict maintenance of a culturally determined separation between facts and values, science and ethics/politics (Wynne 1992, 2001; Jasanoff 2005; Mampuy 2021). Scientists are cast as specialists with the last word in determining whether or not biotechnologies come with risks significant enough to restrict their use, and debates come to a standstill as the concerns of other actors for environmental and socio-economic relationships are rendered less relevant. Even in countries where GMO regulations permit or require considerations of sustainability and ethics, a change towards constructive deliberation is slow in the coming. This roundtable is designed to highlight the value of ecofeminist and relational approaches (Haraway, Bellacasa, Barad) in clarifying and making visible these other actors' concern for environmental and socio-economic consequences of emerging biotechnologies which fall beyond the traditional cultural and scientific perceptual frameworks. It engages specialists working with different aspects of the development, legislation and cultural relationships of gene technology to:

- Identify differences between mechanistic and relational (onto-epistemological) approaches/world views and explain how the former are connected with the fact-value, natural-cultural distinctions that hamper debates on gene technology
- Explore how/why feminist and relational approaches offer better ways of engaging with gene technologies
- Investigate how relational approaches may be included in the regulation and assessment of gene technology

Presenters:

Jennifer Kuzma, North Carolina State University

Zoe Robaey, WUR

Andy Stirling, Science Policy Research Unit, University of Sussex

Trine Antonsen, GenØk

Tim Dassler, GenØk Centre for Biosafety

Session Organizer:

Sigfrid Kjeldaa, GenØk Centre for Biosafety

Chair:

Jérémie McGowan, GenØk Centre for Biosafety

452. Good Relations In Smart Cities: Interplay Between Digitalisation, Governance and Urbanisation

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Governments and the private sector across the world, and increasingly in the global South, are investing both effort and money to build digital infrastructures to enable the adoption of the ostensible technological panacea that is the "smart city." Smart cities have the potential to utilize digital infrastructure and data to improve service provision, monitor development and even mitigate carbon emissions. However, 'good relations' and frameworks of responsibility and solidarity around the transitions to digital governance and technocratic decision-making need to be better understood. This is especially for cities in the global South which face acute issues of marginalization and data-driven inequities. This panel will focus on how "smart cities" are reshaping relations between public institutions, the private sector and urban residents with the potential to marginalize, silence or disadvantage communities in the face of new political-economic nexuses. We welcome empirical, theoretical and methodological papers that address questions including, but not limited to: -What imaginaries are currently being represented in the frameworks of the "smart city"? -How might the datafication of cities change geographies of power in urban spaces? -What is the role of the private sector in provision of 'public' digital infrastructures in smart cities and what are its implications for urban governance? -What role does 'data-driven governance' play in altering access and civic engagement, especially for the most marginalized? -What frameworks are emerging to ensure fairness in the way people are made visible, represented and treated as a result of the use of digital data for urban governance?

Participants:

Body Politics and the Politics of Technology: Technological Experiences among Street-Based Sex Workers in Bangalore

Anant Kamath, National Institute of Advanced Studies (NIAS); *Neethi Padmanabhan*, Indian Institute for Human Settlements (IIHS), Bangalore, India

This paper illustrates how body politics and the politics of technology compound one another for female street-based sex workers (FSSWs) in Bangalore city, India, in their experiences of three technologies – mobile phones, CCTV surveillance, and television media. Mobile phones have emerged as an integral part of street-based sex work in Bangalore as a result of FSSWs abstaining from public spaces that have been overwhelmingly eroded due to neoliberal urban transition over the last two decades in Bangalore. Simultaneously, intensified CCTV surveillance of city spaces keep watch on them, while native-language television media, a techno-cultural predator, routinely conducts self-assigned gentrification operations covertly or overtly discovering and publicly disseminating information on immorality and delinquency. All three technological experiences understandably have had complicated fallout for FSSWs, a result of the politics of technology that are at the foundations of these experiences. The main argument here is that the position of a subaltern informal workers such as FSSWs is complicated not only by the politics of technology (PT), but by the body politics (BP) that intersects that technological experience. This comes about because both PT and BP share strikingly similar concerns in the territories of self, community, support, resistance, negotiation, commerce, and power among FSSWs, which are unravelled in this paper through first-hand narratives from these workers. We also, thereby, contextualize body politics and the politics of technology within the larger literature on sex work, a new perspective presented by this paper.

Homelessness, Spatial Inequalities and the Datafication of Urban Space *Justine Humphry*, University of Sydney; *Chris Chesher*, The University of Sydney

What happens when cities implement technologies of smart governance premised on the extraction of data? What are the impacts of urban datafication on people experiencing homelessness and other marginalised groups? This paper engages with critical data studies, STS scholarship and literature on urban inequalities and public space to make the argument that, with the datafication of urban environments, social and spatial inequalities become further embedded into the logics and infrastructures of cities. The paper draws on ethnographic research into the use of smart street furniture in New York City, Glasgow and London. The first study was carried out in 2018 on LinkNYC, a city-wide network of smart kiosks in New York City. The second study was on InLinkUK kiosks in Glasgow and Strawberry Energy benches in London, carried out in 2019. The studies found that street homeless and other precariously connected citizens rely on these services to maintain access and participate in a digital society but are exposed to new kinds of security and safety risks at the point of connection. We interrogate the relationship between public connectivity and data extraction through these new services, and situate this analysis in the history of oppressive acts of urban policing imposed on people who are homeless as well as the gendered, classed and racialised dynamics of these acts. In conclusion, we propose that establishing 'good relations' in smart cities involves a politics of data that not only addresses the asymmetries of datafication but also the causes of unequal geographies of power in urban space.

Where are smart cities made? Within, beneath, above and beyond the city *Torik Holmes*; *Rebecca Windemer*, Cardiff University

The creation of 'smart' sustainable cities is critical for achieving net zero ambitions. It is thus important to examine how and where smart cities are made and governed. Researchers typically turn to cities with smart aspirations to address such questions, examining local discourses, strategies and sited innovations. We take a different approach. Taking inspiration from science and

technology studies (STS), we follow wires out from Manchester, a city with bold and ambitious ‘smart’ 2038 net zero aspirations. Our approach involves tracing lines of enquiry that start in, cut underneath, reach above and extend beyond the institutional and physical boundaries of the urban area. Along the way, we reveal specific socio-technical points of contingency that are critical for Manchester’s ‘smart’ net zero transition, yet are not explicitly the product of, only about or aimed at supporting this shift. We in turn also show how frameworks of responsibility extend beyond the city, impacting public and private sector relations across various and far-reaching scales. As part of illustrating these issues in reference to Manchester, we argue that revealing and addressing particular frameworks and related contingencies, which are simultaneously distributed across multiple socio-technical networks, is crucial for attempts to accelerate smart city net zero transitions.

Coded jaywalkers and the performativity of smart traffic lights
Pouya Sepehr, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies

In the past two decades “urban science” occurred as an interdisciplinary approach promoting a computational practice of urban management beyond sheer human agency. Various applications under the smart city are stepping into what is termed “automated management.” At this turning point of urban governance, there is a pressing need for critical attention devoted to algorithm’s power and forms of governance it pursues. Algorithms are used to describe, analyse, produce knowledge of everyday life, and predict certain patterns of behaviour. Hence, they manipulate, discipline, and control life by reshaping how people and objects interact in time and space. A growing number of scholarships in STS have started to unpack the situated nature of algorithms and the work they do in reassembling everyday life. In this paper, we aim to empirically study the “smart traffic lights” in Vienna, which seek to automate traffic flow management using camera tracking systems. This technology recognises pedestrians’ intention to cross a street and automatically manages waiting time for them, hence preventing jaywalking and providing better flows of urban traffic. Through a multi-sited ethnography, our analysis starts with focusing on justifications for developing such a technology in the city; then we study the process of computational programming at TU Graz; finally, we revisit nine sites where the traffic lights are implemented as testbeds. Drawing on Lefebvre and Miyazaki, we conduct a rhythm analysis to inquire how the temporality of the city in its different manifestations is being understood and reshaped by these kinds of smart infrastructures.

Smartening Ordinary Citizens: The Narratives of Sejong Smart City Residents in South Korea. *Joëlle Champalet, KAIST (Korea Advanced Institute of Science and Technology)*

Current studies on Smart Cities focus on technical challenges or on the transformation of the governance model between public institutions and urban residents. The narratives depicted in those studies tend to be limited to the envisioned Smart City of the public institution and the voice of strongly engaged citizens. The everyday experiences of ordinary Smart City citizens are then rendered invisible by the power dynamics. Sejong City is a South Korean city whose main construction was achieved around 2016. Originally planned by the Korean government as a Ubiquitous-Eco City, it is still today in the center of the Korean-Smart-City national development. This study explores the narratives of ordinary citizens of Sejong whose daily patterns lead them to cross paths or use smart systems and offers a reflection on how such systems have modified their everyday practices. Semi-structured interviews of Sejong’s inhabitants and the analysis of urban-planning documents produced by the government reveal a gap between the government’s perception and the citizens’ embodied experience of the Smart City. For the government or the planners, the Smart City is a tangible and unified entity that has already come into being, while for the residents it is either an

incomplete project or a future possibility. By analyzing the social acceptability of smart urban environments and the top-down implementation of sustainable behaviors, this paper offers new insights on how the Korean government and planners should engage with urban citizens in the development of Smart City projects.

Session Organizer:

Vikrom Mathur

Chair:

Vikrom Mathur

Discussant:

Ashali Bhandari, Transitions Research

453. Soil Sensing: Methods, politics and experience - I: Novel methods

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

Participants:

An ear to the ground: Soundscapes as a novel methodology for soil research and public engagement with science *Sara Keen, Stanford University; Adrian A Wackett, Stanford University; Travis Clow, Stanford University; Harrison Emma, Stanford University; Jonatan Klaminder, Umea University; Kyungsoo Yoo, University of Minnesota; Jane K Willenbring, Stanford University*

Soil teems with life. Although humans rarely glimpse the organisms living in soils, the above and belowground worlds are tightly interconnected. Soil biota play a critical role in unlocking plant nutrients and mediating soil-atmosphere carbon exchange. Additionally, noise from human activity is perceptible below the surface, which may affect underground organisms that modulate their behavior through sound. Traditionally, studies of soil biota have been restricted to local scales due to time-intensive sampling, and scientific knowledge of soils has been shared primarily through written descriptions, equations, or visual displays. We aim to deepen our scientific knowledge and explore our connection to underground ecosystems with a novel method of soil sensing using near-surface acoustic recordings. We conducted a controlled field experiment in the Swedish Arctic, where we test the basic hypothesis that earthworms alter the soil soundscape as they change soil architecture through tunneling behavior. We find that earthworms affect the underground soundscape and suggest that this method may help to assess soil properties linked to carbon storage. We also observe that noise from distant human activity is audible underground, prompting further questions about the effects of noise on soil biota. Lastly, we suggest that soil soundscapes are a powerful tool for public engagement. Sound is a broadly accessible medium for conveying complex topics: acoustic recordings can be experienced and understood without translation into human language. By allowing others to “eavesdrop” on the underground world, we hope to increase scientific understanding and broaden the community of citizens who engage with soils.

Beyond Munsell: Artistic Contributions to Soil Sensing

Alexandra R. Toland, Bauhaus Universität Weimar; Daniel Wolter, Bauhaus-Universität Weimar

Over the past 20 years, there has been a growing recognition of artistic contributions to soil science and technology studies (e.g., Feller et al., 2015; Wessolek, 2015) and the role of soil in the art world (e.g. Toland, et al. 2018; Adams & Montag, 2016). Collaboration between soil science, arts and humanities disciplines has increased, while new forms of communication and civic engagement have emerged to confront wicked problems of soil pollution, soil organic carbon loss, and soil sealing. At the heart of such sci-art collaborations is an openness towards different methodologies for soil sensing, dating all the way back to Munsell’s attempt to quantify soil color. Drawing on insights

from the field of sensory studies (see, e.g., Howes & Classen, 2014), we examine several case studies that highlight the role artists play in imagining new modes of multi-sensory interaction with soils. The idea is that while soil sensing has become essential for monitoring parameters such as erosion rates and nutrient availability, good data does not necessarily lead to good land use practices or policies. Artistic approaches to soil sensing can create a material and emotional identification with place, foster curiosity and empathy, and reconnect humans to the land, especially in places where connection has been denied or displaced. Soil sensing is discussed here as an aesthetic, embodied engagement with soils that evokes historical understandings of soil as a natural body, in comparison to more contemporary definitions of soil, for example as terrestrial system, carbon sink, or service provider.

“Climate Solutions are Grown in Soil”: Envisioning Soil as Lively Bioinfrastructure for Climate *Tamar Law, Cornell University*

Recently, heightened scrutiny of the ‘invisible crisis beneath our feet’ is bolstered by media proclamations of ‘peak soil’, highlighting vanishing topsoil, the cataclysmic possibility of ‘an end of farming,’ and its severe ramifications for our climate. However, soil is increasingly envisioned as a solution itself to this perilous feedback loop. Part of the expanding litany of nature-based solutions, soil-based innovations are mobilized to regenerate soil’s liveliness and sequester carbon. As soil is ‘made to matter’, specific understandings of what ‘soil’ is and what it does are transforming. Drawing from eight months of ethnographic fieldwork in Central New York State, this paper traces the process and politics of envisioning soil as a climate solution. I describe how soil is envisioned as a lively bioinfrastructure, revealing soils’ vital matter’s role in maintaining soil infrastructure. I consider the biopolitical doubling of this conceptualization, how farmers are conditioned to see soil anew, and in turn, how farmers enact this vision, enrolling soil life to sequester carbon. Ultimately, I reflect on emerging soil relations initiated in this visualization. I demonstrate how such envisioning could amplify capitalist relations to soil, creating new avenues for value, rendering soil investable anew. Simultaneously, I discuss more hopeful relations, through the concept of the soil sublime, describing how aesthetic experience of soil’s lively bioinfrastructure enable different affective and ethical relations to soil. Ultimately, this paper addresses what is at stake in conceptions of soil amid climate change and offers insight into an emergent socio-political ethics of soil care.

Multispecies Design of Fungi Substrates *Lukáš Senft, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Tereza Stockelova, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences; Katerina Kolarova, Institute of Sociology of the Czech Academy of Sciences*

The healing effects of mushrooms have recently become a frequent object of research exploring the ways in which they could treat autoimmune diseases, positively affect the human microbiota and help slowing down neurodegenerative processes. The value of the world’s annual production of medicinal mushrooms is estimated at billions of dollars. This demand calls for new modes of the mushrooms production. In this paper, we follow the work of Mr. Hruška, an agricultural engineer who, together with his students, designs specific substrates for different medicinal mushrooms. Crucial part of the endeavour is finding the right balance between substrate sterilization and substrate fermentation that will create opportunities for bacteria and fungi to cooperate. While the researchers are trying to control the characteristics of the substrate, it is not completely tamed. Fungi substrate is an outcome of interplay between biotic and abiotic forces thus involving both intentional and unintentional design (Tsing, 2015) engendered by human and

more-than-human participants. While Tsing examines an economy based on the foraging of wild mushrooms, we ask what (different) gift/commodity circulation is implied by and in the designed substrate? What is reduced and what is amplified (Latour, 1999) in the process of designing a more nutritious, yet relatively enclosed system of the substrate that would best support the spread of fungi and that would lead to the prosperity of the desired mushrooms? Latour, B. Pandora’s Hope, 1999. Tsing, A.L. The Mushroom at the End of the World, 2015.

Sedimentary Legacy for Soil Science: from Natural to Socio-Ecological *David Ribes, University of Washington; Shana Lee Hirsch, University of Washington; Sarah Catherine Inman, University of Washington*

This talk tracks the transition and tribulations of soil from a biogeophysical scientific object, to a socio-ecological scientific object. Generally, ecological science can be characterized as on a trajectory to accepting the socioecological view, but this transition has been persistently hampered by a long-legacy of instruments, data and specimens that exclusively target biogeophysical phenomena. We focus on the changing resources -- such as data and specimens -- that scientists have amassed across the years to investigate these shifting ontologies for soil. We argue that soil research (and long-term research more generally) displays a ‘sedimentary legacy’: even as new data and specimen collections are added, older collections continue to exert persistent and consequential influences on contemporary research. Ultimately, this puts socioecology on a challenging uphill trajectory to establish its scientific claims, though not a hopeless one.

Tracing Memory: Rediscovering Our Relationship with Soil *Jude Allen, Soil Voices*

Both culturally and physiologically, humans are integrally linked to the soil. As the place where we posit the dead, soil contains remnants of all we ever were. Soil bears human and animal imprints, holding traces of our very recent interactions with the ground beneath us, while at the same time, it holds fossilised remains of the first forms of life and archaeological evidence of ancient human activity. Furthermore, as the origin of everything that we nourish ourselves with, soil also makes us. Questioning modern Western assumptions regarding human identity and individuality, this paper will argue the notion that humans, like all the other organisms on this planet, are part of a collective cycle, both somatic and cognitive, of which soil plays a significant part. Drawing on Julia Kristeva’s notion of the abject, and Mary Douglas’ work on purity and pollution, I suggest our relationship with soil has become a site of cultural horror. As a result of such abhorrence, I explore how we have become estranged not only from soil, but also from our own selves. I shall conclude with a discussion of a collaborative project, Soil Voices, which seeks to reconnect humans to soil in a positive way through memories and oral histories of people’s relationships with soil.

Session Organizer:

Sebastian Ureta, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

Chair:

Daniel Walls, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Discussant:

Abby Kinchy, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

454. Trans STS: An Emerging and Continuing Field

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

This panel seeks to conceptualize the beginnings of trans STS as a field. We will explore some of the origins of trans STS, such as critiquing medicalized discourses, but mostly focus our attention to the current state of the field. We broadly define trans STS as a way of understanding trans and gender as both institutional sites of control and as individual and

collective resistance; an epistemology of communities, and ultimately a technology of state discipline and collective liberation. Trans STS largely looks at the intersections between neoliberal institutions and states, and the resistance and transformation of those structures by trans people, with the ultimate goal of improving relations between them. The panel will examine how trans STS scholars engage with and relate to different subfields of STS and how other subfields of STS could connect to and benefit from trans STS. In particular we will focus on trans STS as it relates to medicalization, incarceration, and informatics. In this panel, we'll explore questions of: What does trans STS mean? What can trans STS take up as objects of study? How does it fit in the larger field? How can trans STS address the relationship between medicalization and trans subjectivity without reifying the focus on the trans body and medicalization? What kinds of scholarship already exists that might already fit into the trans STS field, and what further research could occur?

Participants:

Digital Pronouns: Using and sharing pronouns as gender classification practices *Tristan Gohring, Indiana University - Bloomington*

This paper investigates the role of pronouns and pronoun sharing practices as part of gender infrastructure and classification. Based on in-depth qualitative interviews about the design and implementation of digital tools for pronoun sharing, I discuss the sociotechnical imaginaries surrounding pronoun use and sharing. Pronouns are not the same thing as gender identity, but people do tend to see them as a marker of gender. We can see the increasingly popular practice of pronoun sharing as an interruption/intervention into the daily process of gendering others according to our assumptions about their appearance/name/clothing. Sharing one's pronouns is an act of asserting gender identity (or at least something related to it) rather than allowing others to decide gender identity for myself. Making a habit of this in a work setting creates a gendering process that runs more or less parallel to the formal part of gender classification that takes place in the realm of identification and employment documents. We can see the development of pronoun sharing as an example of a rupture in the traditional process of gender classification, which helps illuminate the process and work of gender classification.

Creation of the trans subject through the medicalization and resistance *Kate Shindle, Indiana University Department of Gender Studies*

The medicalization of trans bodies has been a subject of trans studies since its inception, but recently trans studies scholars have incorporated STS methodologies into their critiques of medicalization. Trans STS that interrogates medicalization take particular care to explore the intersections of race and class as shaping the understandings of gender, both cis and trans. While the methods and themes vary for each scholar, they all explore several main questions that I'll cover in detail. What does it mean to be trans, in terms of how society, medicine and institutions see and understand trans people, and how trans people themselves understand themselves? How were the categories of gender, sex, and cis versus trans created, both within a medical context and in resistance to these medical definitions? How does medicalization conceptualize the overlaps between intersex and trans individuals, through their resistance to binaries? How does medicalization create a desubjectified subject, and how do we see resistance to this? How do trans and intersex subjects move in the world and negotiate the restrictions and barriers within cis-tems, and within trans and intersex communities outside of these institutions? These questions allow scholars to utilize STS theorizations and understand trans as a creation of medicalization, resistance, community, and technology, making it a variable entity that can both be mobilized by institutions for control and subordination, and can be reclaimed by individuals as a form of empowerment and resistance.

Criminal Diagnoses: Examining Medicopsychiatric

Constructions of Gender Deviance in Federal Inmates 1930-1960 *Vic Overdorf, Indiana University*

This paper examines U.S. carceral history as a site for trans STS by interrogating the networks of power that created and sustained medicalized discourse about "normal" and "deviant" gender identity in prisons. In the case of early-to-mid twentieth century prisons, medical and psychiatric institutions served as gender norming mechanisms, rendering those who did not conform as "sick" or "psychotic." This paper shows that medical and psychiatric power in prisons was exercised through targeted medical examinations and psychiatric reports conducted by prison physicians. Diagnoses such as "sexual psychopathy" and "sexual perversion" were employed to mark gender and sexual deviance, and to justify maltreatment of gender non-conforming prisoners. These individualized medical and psychiatric pursuits contributed not only to the criminalization of incarcerated individuals, but also to the criminalization of the communities who fell within the categories of deviance constructed and sustained by these institutions. This paper looks specifically at the experiences of individuals incarcerated for Sodomy in federal prisons between the years of 1930 and 1960. Trans STS, this paper argues, is a framework through which we can explore the gendered specificities of LGBT prisoners' encounters with institutional power.

Session Organizer:

Kate Shindle, Indiana University Department of Gender Studies

455. Human-Computer Entanglements: Psychology, Computing, and Artificial Intelligence in the 20th Century

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

For the past eighty years, computing and the human sciences have been closely interconnected: computers have been perceived as augmenting, complementing, and, in some cases, entirely supplanting human minds. While scholars have long acknowledged the military-industrial context in which digital computers emerged, only recently they started problematizing how human-computer systems reflect the dominant imagination of what it means to be human. This panel investigates four episodes in the history of human-computer systems, which reveal a situated conception of human cognition that reflects the social epistemologies of "the human" contemporary to the moment of their design. Together, they demonstrate that during the period between 1950 and 1980, computer engineers did not pursue their agenda as a unified and autonomous discipline. By contrast, system designers drew liberally on the humanities and the social sciences—especially psychology—to guide their research. This panel explores how notions thought to be the hallmark of advanced cognition, such as "learning" and "creativity," were given a material instantiation in specific computer systems. Likewise, researchers undertook detailed studies of human operators, counting, classifying, qualifying, and modelling them as "users." This suggests that the place of the human in the history of computing is not so much to be discovered as rediscovered. An interdisciplinary eye on the rich historical archive of technical reports, scientific publications, design documents, and experimental protocols unpacks how sedimented prejudices and aspirational visions about humanity have shaped human-computer systems, and highlights what is at stake when researchers strive to model humanity in code and silicon.

Participants:

The Duality of the Personal Computer User: Psychologists and Secretaries at Xerox PARC, 1973-1983 *Sam Schirvar, History and Sociology of Science, University of Pennsylvania*

This paper explores the practice of early psychology research in Human-Computer Interaction (HCI) and contextualizes it in the gendered labor process of American office work in the 1970s. When researchers at Xerox Palo Alto Research Center (PARC) started imagining who would operate their individualized computers in the early 1970s, they saw the secretaries around them as typical novice users. Following Herbert Simon and Allen

Newell's study of problem solving, researchers at PARC's Applied Information-Processing Psychology Project (AIP) constructed psychological models of computer use by studying secretaries editing manuscripts on Xerox's prototype computers. However, by the early 1980s, this group saw secretaries as exceptional users—people whose traditional relationship with machinery could be antithetical to who a “user” was. Previous scholarship has shown how computer designers' reflexive understanding of the user as an intellectual worker like themselves transformed when designers encountered the “real,” novice users at PARC, people who lacked technical expertise. This paper explores AIP's correspondence, published works, internal reports, and experimental protocol to expand our understanding of this transition. Constructing a psychological model of different office occupants as “users” involved grappling not only with different levels of technical skill but also with possible conflicts between autonomy and control: personal computer users were both managers and managed.

Programming the Creative Mind: Cognitive Psychology and the PLATO Computer in the 1960s-1970s *Ekaterina Babintseva, Harvey Mudd College*

In 1964, University of Illinois psychologist Jack Easley joined the team of computer engineers at the Coordinated Sciences Laboratory (CSL) to turn the educational computer PLATO (Programmed Logical for Automated Teaching Operations) into a machine that would teach students how to think creatively. Funded by ARPA, Easley used PLATO as an instrument in his research on cognition and man-machine interaction. This paper traces ten years of Easley's collaboration with CSL and his changing theories of whether computers were compatible with the mind's creative nature. Easley was a part of the cognitive movement in American psychology that sought to provide a formal description of the gamut of mental operations that stand behind creative thinking. At first, Easley sought to encode the cognitive account of the human mind into the PLATO software, sharing CSL's belief that the cognitive perspective could turn PLATO into an instrument of streamlining human creativity. However, by the late 1970s, Easley became disappointed in PLATO's potential to harness human capacity to reason creatively. He identified the cognitive approach as the major source of the problem, blaming it for offering an inadequate account of how humans think. Concerned with the adult mind, it ignored the specificities of developing cognition. Additionally, as demonstrated in Easley's experimental work, the cognitive approach failed to consider the subject's physical experience of the world. Drawing on archival materials, this case study explicates the shaping role of cognitive psychology and the paradigmatic notion of the disembodied adult mind in the development of mid-century computing.

Two Musical Episodes at the Piano Keyboard in the Study of Human Information-Processing: Information as “Cognitive Good” in Interdisciplinary Research *Eamonn Bell, Durham University*

In the early 1950s, the biologist Henry Quastler asked pianists to sight-read randomly generated musical scores as quickly and as accurately as possible. Quastler computed their performance as their “information transmission rate”, measured in bits-per-second across a variety of related tachistoscopic tasks. Later, Walter Reitman and Marta Sánchez, working at the Carnegie Institute of Technology, made tape recordings of a composer “thinking aloud” as they composed a fugue at the piano keyboard. Reitman (1965) analyzed this data to inspire the design of Argus, a new computer model of “human information-processing” that complemented the paradigmatic early AI research of his colleagues Newell and Simon (1956). Drawing on archival material, I argue that it was “information”—perhaps the most fungible post-World War II “cognitive good” (Bod et al. 2019)—that facilitated such interdisciplinary research in human

psychology during the heyday of first-order cybernetics, integrating music into the burgeoning cognitive sciences. Musical behavior is leveraged in both experimental systems (Rheinberger 1997) as a proxy for some facet of cognition otherwise indirectly observable: a presumed human “channel capacity” and the ability to creatively solve “ill-defined problems”, respectively. Where Quastler standardized experimental subjects across sensory modalities and study cohorts using the mathematics of information theory, Reitman used the radically inter-subjective protocol study to probe reasoning as information-processing in a less explicitly quantitative way. The detail of such similarities and differences is disclosed by a tightly integrated view on the twinned fates of the humanities and the sciences, here afforded by the liaisons between music and cybernetics. References: Bod, Rens, Jeroen van Dongen, Sjang L. ten Hagen, Bart Karstens, and Emma Mojet. “The Flow of Cognitive Goods: A Historiographical Framework for the Study of Epistemic Transfer.” *Isis* 110, no. 3 (September 2019): 483–96. <https://doi.org/10.1086/704673>. Newell, Allen, and Herbert Simon. “The Logic Theory Machine—A Complex Information Processing System.” *IRE Transactions on Information Theory* 2, no. 3 (1956): 61–79. Reitman, Walter R. *Cognition and Thought: An Information-Processing Approach*. New York: Wiley, 1965. Rheinberger, Hans-Jörg. *Toward a History of Epistemic Things: Synthesizing Proteins in the Test Tube*. Stanford, CA: Stanford University Press, 1997.

“Production of Completely New Ideas not Deducible from Known Data”: Human Creative Activity as Early Machine Learning *Aaron Louis Mendon-Plasek, Columbia University*

Focusing on a collection of working practices, computing devices, and research problems dubbed “machine learning” as early as 1953, this paper reconstructs 1950s and 1960s machine learning through a series of attempts to build “creative” learning machines. In principle, for these engineers and mathematicians, “creativity” was the ability to identify what was contextually “significant” to the successful performance of a task. In practice, this “creativity” was operationalized by mid-twentieth century pattern recognition researchers as the capacity to make efficacious judgments given new, messy data. Such “creative” learning machines had the possibility of performing a task that a programmer did not explicitly instruct the computer to do, and so, researchers hoped, might learn to do something even the programmer did not know how to do. Beginning with early 1950s computing experiments in reinforcement learning performed by women and men and subsequent transnational efforts to mechanize “hypothesis formation” using Bayesian statistics in the 1960s, creativity in both humans and machines was linked to the ability to produce new “contexts” from the same data. The synecdoche of creativity as context-swapping distinguished early machine learning from coeval enterprises in artificial intelligence and cybernetics, and encouraged problem-framing strategies that enabled learning machines to robustly respond even when new information contradicted previous data. Contemporary claims about the efficacy of machine learning (or lack thereof) depend upon but rarely interrogate the tacit historical notion of creativity this paper makes explicit.

Session Organizers:

Ekaterina Babintseva, Harvey Mudd College
Eamonn Bell, Durham University

Chair:

Joy Lisi Rankin

Discussant:

Charles Luke Alan Stark

456. Ferment as Method: Creating the Conditions for Transformative Relations - III

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Where the 2020 pandemic prompted new desires for hyper-sterile environments, it also sparked interest in the microbe-rich world of fermentation. Home kitchens, wiped clean with bleach and sanitizer, produced effervescent brews, doubling sourdoughs, and funky sauerkrauts. Fermentation provided a collaborative ‘contamination’ (Tsing 2015) that prompted experimentation, care, and new forms of sustenance amid loss, isolation, and precarity. In fermentation microbes transform their substrates and each other into new forms, textures, flavors, aromas, and matters. Practicing fermentation invites open-ended collaboration across species boundaries; requiring attention (when is it ferment and when is it rot?), care (who needs more water, more food, more salt?), and a willingness for all parties to be changed by the process (no one is coming out the same as they went in) (Fournier 2020, Maroney 2018, Villalba 2019). Fermentation is more than a material process; ideas, people, and movements ferment. The concept offers a rich metaphor that captures the energy of activists, and transformative potential at any scale. Since ferments can also turn sour, go awry, become toxic, and foment violence and trouble, as a metaphor for responsible change, it contains its own limits. This panel invites participants to ferment as a method in their STS projects. How does thinking with fermentation foreground new configurations of interdependence and care in our work? How might a slower process that allows for unexpected results affect our means of producing knowledge? Might such a method, emergent in the becoming together, open up space to foster ‘good’ relations or challenge ‘bad’ ones?

Participants:

Cross-Contaminations: Fermenting Food and Relations in Northern Italy *Janita Van Dyk, University of Toronto*

My paper explores ethnographically how and in what ways literal fermentation became a process and a concept for students to think with at the Slow Food university in Northern Italy, in and out of the classroom. This university is known for training students from around the world in gastronomy, agricultural sciences, and the culinary arts. Here, students learned about fermentation as everything from composting techniques used by market gardeners to a highly regulated process of manufacturing Parmigiano Reggiano. Students made miso in student labs and experimented with kombuchas in apartment kitchens. However, fermentation became more than just a practice; it was also a way students worked through the complex gendered, classed, and racialized boundaries of complex agricultural systems and their relationships between themselves and more-than-human landscapes and worlds—fermentation allowed cross-contaminations. In other words, lessons in literal fermentation were transformed into metaphors and models for organizing social and ecological life, but not without tensions. In this paper, I will explore some of these transformations—how fermentation as a material practice was ‘fermented’ to think about different social and ecological relations, and when and how openness to the metaphorical and physical cross-contaminations inherent to fermentation were engaged, managed, or resisted.

Fermentation as a method for doing otherwise *Salla Sariola, University of Helsinki*

This presentation ferments together two different sets of fermentation fieldwork material – among sourdough bakers in Finland, Northern of Europe, and rice beer makers among indigenous groups in Assam, India, close to the border with Myanmar. By juxtaposing the two sets of practices, the paper attempts to explore cultures of cultures – the social of microbes and the microbes of social practices. With some crucial differences, both described fermentation as a process that necessitates a more-than-human framing that foregrounds microbes as central characters. Fermentation practitioners’ lay theories of microbes are not merely microbiological but present cultural analysis situated in the political climate of increasing populism in both Europe and India, as well as the Earthly destruction sometimes named as the Anthropocene. The paper describes the fermenters putting forward critiques of capitalism that link ecological extraction, political oppression, and industrial health care and food production. While advancing the field of

social study of microbes and contributing to broader discussions within Environmental Humanities, Feminist Technoscience and Indigenous Studies, the paper shows how fermentation as the subject of process-based analysis connects across various scales, and with the notion of diffraction (Barad 2007) enables a discussion of the complex entanglements of the material and social/political.

Interplanetary Fermentation *Maggie Coblenz, Massachusetts Institute for Technology (MIT)*

What can we learn from the practice of fermentation, to create new narratives for space futures and engage alternative approaches to health and wellbeing, in space and beyond? A new era of space exploration is focused back on the Moon. In order to support future crews, space agencies will need to address the complex requirements of long-duration missions while in lunar orbit or on the surface of the Moon, and this includes how to provide future crews with safe, nutritious food for survival. What is at risk of being lost when engineering constraints are the sole driver of innovation? In order to welcome a multifaceted cohort of people into space and build communities with care, we need to consider a variety of ingredients and prepare the tools to cook, share and save food. In space, the method of fermentation could not only help preserve limited fresh ingredients and grow nutrients, but also provide opportunities for caretaking, relationships with non-human life, and sensory interactions (i.e. flavour and aroma). Through the lens of food, this research prompts a more nuanced debate about the skills and tools required to live on the Moon, to make room for community wellbeing, embodied knowledge, and creative expression.

Productive Rot: Summoning Natural Processes for Other-than-natural Ends. *Xan Sarah Chacko, Wellesley College*

When collections of seed arrive at the seed bank laboratory, they go through a long and careful process of ‘purification’ from natural specimens to laboratory facts that can be quantified and commodified for their future use. Since ‘nothing comes without its world’ and only seeds end up in the frozen vault, great pains are taken to separate them from their worlds and make seeds legible through the seed bank systems of valuation. Sometimes whole fruit arrive as part of collections and as part of this extractive process of ‘constitutive cleaning’ they are allowed to ferment in the holding rooms till they fall apart. Sorting through this funky mess of fizzy fruit pulp to separate out the seeds is a day long process that requires everyone at the bank pitch in to make the work go faster. In this paper I think with this moment of ferment, this conviviality of seed bank labour—gendered, technical, and creative. While these scientists are engaged in the odorous work of separating seed from fruit, they are getting entangled with the seeds and each other through shared space, jokes, and bodily pains. How might the seed bank, with its neocolonial symbolic position as ‘a caretaker of the world’s plants’, also be a space of hope, fun, and laughter. As the fruit in the seed bank laboratory ferments, it draws curators into a shared effervescent bodily practice that requires attention to sensations and smells—all the while participating in the extraction of seeds from their worlds.

Session Organizer:

Xan Sarah Chacko, Wellesley College

Chair:

Susannah Chapman, School of Social Science, The University of Queensland

457. Governing Environmental Inequalities: Towards a New Research-Action Framework on Agency, Power & Multispecies Justice – III: Biodiversity, Conservation & Technoscience

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:

Living with Wilderness? Rewilding and the Problems of "Nature." *Taylor Dotson, New Mexico Tech*

Some scientists believe that declining biodiversity poses an existential threat to humanity, one equal to that of climate change. But whether or not a sixth "mass extinction event" is actually underway remains hotly disputed. Rewilding has emerged over the last decades as an alternative proposal for ameliorating the anthropogenic harms falling on non-domesticated species. Definitions of the concept vary considerably, but most center on the idea of "making room" for non-human nature, emphasizing non-human agency in ecosystem processes as generative of emergent and resilient self-organization, and the call to learn to live with wilderness rather than outside it. This talk works through some of the political problematics of rewilding: Who exactly makes room for what wilderness and where? Who speaks for non-human agency? What does it mean to live with wilderness? And whose lifeways are expected to give way and whose are to provide guidance? But STS academic analysis alone will not be capable of resolving these problematics, if the tensions within rewilding are even reconcilable. I argue that the role of STS and allied fields for contentious and emerging forms of technoscience, such as rewilding, is to focus on providing appropriate expertise and on supporting the development of policymaking approaches that are both prudent and less generative of inequity.

The Albany Pine Bush, a Landscape of Modernity: Rethinking the 'Ecosystem' in the Anthropocene *Katherine Michele Tote, University at Albany, SUNY*

The Albany Pine Bush (APB), located in New York's Capital Region, is among the largest of few surviving inland pine barrens in the world. Inundated with commercial and residential development in the late 20th century, this ecoregion has been the site of environmental controversy for decades. In 1980, a local biologist proclaimed to a regional newspaper that, if a new shopping mall were to be constructed in the area as planned, local wildlife would cease to exist. That shopping mall was indeed built, but environmentalists and anti-development community organizations also saw victory with the concomitant establishment of a large recreational nature preserve, maintained with scheduled burns and comprehensive invasive species management. Native wildlife, such as the flagship endangered Karner Blue butterfly -- first identified as a subspecies by lepidopterist-cum-author Vladimir Nabokov -- continue to thrive in the APB, coexisting alongside the million-square-foot shopping mall, the world's largest Walmart, eight-lane interstate highways, and the brutalist skylines of State-owned campuses that stand in stark contrast with Catskill ridges visible on a clear day. As we look toward a sustainable future, it is critical that 'development' and 'conservation' are considered within in a framework of symbiotic coexistence -- there is no longer (and perhaps there never was) a clear distinction between human and nature. This paper uses the APB as a case study to explore the complex landscapes of modernity, the shortcomings of traditional environmentalism, and the power of various actors, both human and non-human, in shaping the shared ecosystems of the Anthropocene.

Are we in the same mountain? The political ontology of conservation in the Colombian high Andean mountains *Camilo Castillo, Department of Thematic Studies - Technology and Social Change, Linköping University*

Páramos are among the most important ecosystems of the northern Andes in South America. The provision of water for millions of people there depends on these unique high mountain ecosystems, which in turn are also the refuge for a rich biodiversity. That is the case in Colombia, where páramos encompass a variety of relationships for many people: as 'Islands of the sky' are known among biologists, or 'biodiversity

hotspots' in conservation agendas, but they are also a 'territory' for campesinos communities that found in these remote mountains a safe place after fleeing from political violence in the 19th and 20th centuries. The need to protect páramos is uncontroversial, but the attempts to do it has been conflictive. When the Colombian government tried to regulate the conservation of páramos through a cartography and biological samplings, it was clear that the páramo of the regulation was not compatible with the presence of campesinos, despite they have been there for generations cultivating more-than-human environments with plants, animals, mountains, books, instruments and more. When biologists, campesinos, public officers, maps, plants, and fragile ecosystems do not seem to fit together in conservation agendas, issues of political ontology and environmental justice are at stake. In this paper I analyze how the conservation of páramos in Colombia is possible through the assemblage of concrete sociotechnical practices that disproportionately affect historically excluded communities and their more-than-human worlds, it also interrogates about the possibility to reconstruct an environmentally just conservation attentive to scientific practices, environmental history, ontology and more-than-human relationships.

Session Organizer:

William San Martín, Worcester Polytechnic Institute (WPI)

Chair:

Martín Fonck, Rachel Carson Center for Environment and Society

Discussant:

Ashawari Chaudhuri, National University of Singapore (NUS)

458. AI and Feminist STS - I

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Much excellent work has documented how contemporary artificial intelligence (AI) systems reinforce and deepen historical inequalities and oppressions. Further work remains, however, on whether and how AI systems can do otherwise. Recent social movements within AI research have begun to politicize AI technologies and their entanglements with social justice, power relations, and environmentalism (see, for example, #TechWontBuildIt and recent ACM special issues on "AI Activism" and "Green AI"). In a current technology ecosystem dominated by commercial and military interests, however, few possibilities seem to exist for AI practitioners to "strive towards good relations" among humans, technologies, and environments. This panel seeks to investigate how theories, methods, and ways of knowing from decades of feminist STS scholarship can inform the study of AI systems as they are used today. In Alison Adam's (1995) feminist critique of AI epistemology, she emphasizes the need for more concrete examples of a "successor science" based on feminist epistemology and social constructivism to ground AI research. What would "successor AI" look like, built on principles of situated knowledges and standpoint theory? Beyond universalized, depoliticized notions of "ethical AI," might an analysis using feminist STS ground AI systems in complex sociotechnical entanglements and particular histories, geographies, communities, and contexts? This panel features work that engages with these questions and imagines new possibilities for feminist AI technologies. Topics include, but are not limited to, the following: * Social and political movements that aim to centre ethics of care, entanglement, relationality, and responsibility in human-AI systems * Indigenous, Black, feminist, and queer conceptualizations of "artificial intelligence" * Disability studies, feminist STS, and artificial intelligence * Ecofeminism, environmental justice, "green AI" and environmental impacts of AI systems * Standpoint theory and the politics of image, speech, and emotion recognition systems * Intersections and contradictions between feminist health projects and AI in healthcare * New methods and imagined futures for feminist, de-/anti-colonial, anti-military, anti-carceral, anti-capitalist AI Keywords: feminist STS, artificial intelligence, technofeminism, feminist technologies, ethical AI

Participants:

Caring for Automated Systems in Digital Game Development
Aleena Chia, Simon Fraser University

This paper looks at how game developers frame procedural content generation (PCG) as automation of creativity. By producing scalable results with combinatorial diversity, PCG are touted as the future of content, yet flouted as the harbinger of technological unemployment in the future of creative work. However, the real danger of automating creativity is not job loss per se, but the constitution of a underclass of artists, writers, and musicians, whose cognitive work are deemed “manual” and relegated to maintain and be managed by automated tools and those who design them. The creative work of this underclass—disproportionately performed by racialized, minoritized, feminized, and outsourced labour—is seen as derivative, expendable, and interchangeable with automatic processes. Drawing from a qualitative analysis of trade discourses about PCG, this paper engages with the maintenance of automated systems in creative industries through feminist approaches to care as distributed across multiple agencies and relational obligations (Puig de la Bellacasa 2017). Instead of smoothing over irresolvable—material and ideological—tensions in automation, care is situational, improvisational, and even unruly. Care is a vital source of friction (Tsing 2005) in automation’s impetus towards standardization and integration in complex production pipelines. Care implicates tools, their makers and their users in everyday decisions about conditions of labour and purposes of creation. Putting research on creative industries in conversation with recent work on platform labour and algorithmic management, this paper asks how the care of automated tools can be leveraged for system design.

'Green AI,' Technofeminism, and Environmental Justice *Rachel Bergmann, Microsoft Research New England*

This paper explores and analyzes the recent resurgence of interest in the US research community on the environmental impact of computing systems, specifically AI and natural language processing. In December 2020, Communications of the ACM published a special issue on the promises of “Green AI”; the same week, leading AI ethics researcher Timnit Gebru was fired from Google over a paper critical of the environmental costs of large language models. Although computational sustainability has been an area of computer science research for decades, AI is approaching somewhat of an environmental turn, not necessarily commensurable with the dominant logics of big data, commercialism and unbridled growth. Using theoretical frameworks drawn from technofeminism (Wajcman, 1991) and materialist ecofeminism (Merchant, 1990), I critically examine this moment of AI environmentalism within ethical AI research, investigating which questions are and are not asked; which methods are used; communities and geographies prioritized; the kinds of conclusions reached; and whom and what they ultimately benefit (Tikka, in Vakoch & Mickey, 2018). I turn to recent work on Indigenous protocols and artificial intelligence (Lewis et al, 2020), as well as histories of coalition-based environmental justice movements in the US Southwest, to offer further directions toward which this “AI environmentalism” can grow. These protocols and histories, I argue, can help scholars situate AI systems in place and environment, and they can provide insight into designing AI systems in solidarity with coalitional and community-led contemporary environmental justice movements.

How a Gendered Startup Culture Reinforces Heteronormativity in AI *Hyejin Jo, Simon Fraser University, Communication*
AI (artificial intelligence) techniques are rapidly evolved in their form, which raises the significance of ethical decision-making in AI. Many scholars across the field of studies, including STS, have a keen interest in AI ethics brought by the gendered machine learning and decision-making processes. In this regard, this paper intends to argue that unethical decision-making

procedure embedded in AI machine learning is more associated with the sociotechnical relations between humans and their practices, not between humans and computing technology. More specifically, this paper critically examines how a group of young heterosexual males in an AI startup company reinforces heteronormative values in their technology embedded in the new startup culture. Through a case study, as a research method, of Lee Luda, an AI chatbot representing a female in her 20s, made by SCATTER LAB, and its debate, this paper contributes to the fundamental questions and discussion about male dominance in technology, heteronormativity as a gendered practice, and misogynist and racist corporate cultures in technology. From a feminist STS perspective, this research addresses the following questions: 1) How is heteronormativity in AI perpetuated by a young and male-dominant startup company and its culture? 2) Who is benefitting? In response to these items, this paper anticipates how a feminist STS responds and suggests a refined approach against patriarchal corporate cultures and technology.

How Computers See: The Gaze from Nowhere *Emily Denton, Google; Alex Hanna, Google; Razvan Amironesei, Google; Hilary Nicole, Google*

Benchmark datasets form the backbone of machine learning research and development: they formalize machine learning tasks by specifying the ideal input-output mapping on a set of exemplar data instances; they operate as measurement devices, allowing researchers to compare algorithms and benchmark progress on a particular problem; and they play a critical role in orienting research agendas within particular academic communities. Datasets are regularly incorporated into the daily routines of machine learning practitioners -- easily imported with a line of code -- yet critical engagement with the politics and values embedded within them is far rarer. In this sense, datasets operate as naturalized infrastructure underlying machine learning practice. Despite being frequently treated as value-neutral scientific tools, machine learning datasets can be better understood as situated, constructed, and political artifacts. They have been constructed and labored upon by individuals -- the developers, data annotators, and others -- situated in varied personal, disciplinary, and institutional contexts. Datasets embed particular world views -- views that are shaped by subject positions of those involved in their development as well as the sociotechnical infrastructures leveraged to construct them. In this work we focus our attention on image classification datasets, using Imagenet as an exemplar. We examine how current practices of dataset development and use serve to obfuscate the inherently contextual and situated nature of these datasets. We also examine how the discourses that surround these datasets often wield naturalistic rhetoric, casting the subjective and contextual categorizations as universal, objective, or self-evident. By failing to account for the particularities of prominent benchmark datasets -- particularities that often reflect a white, Western, male gaze -- we understand these datasets as a technical instantiation of Haraway's “god trick”, the view that “sees everything from nowhere”. We examine the consequences of this highly concentrated “view from nowhere” for data subjects and those impacted by image classification tools developed from these datasets.

Session Organizer:

Rachel Bergmann, Microsoft Research New England

Discussant:

Os Keyes, University of Washington

459. “Won’t you be my neighbor?”: Towards Theory and Ethics in Society

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

STS has studied such diverse technoscientific domains as agriculture and GMOs, biotechnology, climate science and geoengineering, nuclear energy,

and security. Beyond these practical sites, STS methods can equally be applied to a range of philosophical fields that do not yet fully engage with STS analysis, including domains of theory (e.g. democratic, political, social) and ethics (e.g. moral philosophy). The papers collected in this panel extend STS's critical horizons to engage neighboring fields by investigating theory and ethics at work in society. Thus, we subvert the widely presumed relationship between STS and theory. Instead of STS using the tools of political, social and moral theory to make sense of its objects of analysis, we show how "theory" can be itself an object of STS analysis and how it can take on board fundamental STS insights about practice and methodology. We ask how social practices can matter for grounding theory and ethics in social constructions rather than in philosophical abstractions. How can the STS methodological commitment to symmetry--between science/technology and society--make sense of theories and ethics as thought and practiced in the world? We explore theory and ethics by looking not only at what theorists and ethicists say about the world, but at what they do to construct the world in relation to society's empirically demonstrated normative commitments. As such, theory appears as much of a force for constructing the world as technoscientific practice--and STS an equally powerful analytical guide towards the desired ends of democracy and justice.

Participants:

Ethics by Explanation: Transactional underpinnings of "Explainable AI" *Margarita Boenig-Liptsin, Human Contexts and Ethics Program, Division of Computing, Data Science, and Society, UC Berkeley*

A core feature of "ethical Artificial Intelligence (AI)" recommendations and frameworks is "explainability." Explainability aims to make it possible for the human user to understand the way in which the model works and how it computes the output in order that people can integrate the model into their own chain of action. An explainable model allows the human to take responsibility for the action by making socio-technical action with algorithms comprehensible to the human. Explainability as an ethical principle thus reveals an understanding of human action as goal-oriented and transactional. Action, in this view, unfolds outwards from a human or machine that sets things in motion, as a sequence of handoffs between humans and machines, before it is completed in an intended way. In this paper I compare the ways in which this transactional concept of action is taken up in ethical principles and practices for AI in the United States and in France/European Union. I look at how explainability is operationalized in legal and ethical doctrine as well as encoded by companies into "explainable AI" products and services. In these two different cultural and epistemic environments, how is explainability put into practice, by whom, explaining what to whom? And how can STS-inflected ethical theory support a way to overcome the limitations of explainability, and its underlying theory of ethical action?

Hi Ethicist, what are you cooking?: 'In-House-Ethics' in Silicon Valley and Beyond *Kasper Hedegaard Schiölin, Harvard STS Program, Harvard Kennedy School*

Democratizing Ethics: Engaging STS with Nussbaum's "Tragic Question" *Karen Huang, Georgetown University*

STS can broaden its critical horizons to examine moral theory as a domain of knowledge. STS approaches to ethics start from publics, not philosophers, as sources of epistemic and moral authority. In this way, STS democratizes ethics by analyzing what ethics looks like in society. This paper first examines efforts to democratize ethics within moral philosophy, examining in particular work done by the burgeoning area of "experimental ethics". This empirical tradition questions intuition as a method in philosophy, and justifies the experimental study of moral judgments by appealing to democratic theory on public polling. I discuss how this turn to empirical ethics located at the psychological level has further naturalized moral dilemmas through a reification of individual choice. I argue that STS

methods can broaden the horizon of empirical ethics by providing a lens to analyze social and institutional practices, and thereby question abstractions of individual choice assumed by moral philosophy. STS approaches, aligning with recent anthropological approaches in ethics, examine structural affordances enabling and constraining moral dilemmas. In this way, STS bypasses what Nussbaum calls the ordinary question of "What shall we do?" to the tragic question of "Is any of the available options free from serious moral wrongdoing?" The tragic question thus invites public deliberation on the structural conditions underlying taken-for-granted moral dilemmas of individual choice. In so doing, STS democratizes ethics not through a theory of public polling, but through a theory of public deliberation. STS thus offers a democratic normative framework for ethics in society.

Global Warming, Global Market: Science, Economics, and Ethics in the Anthropocene *Stefan Schäfer, Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies*

The concept of the Anthropocene has come under fire for flattening historical time. Critics argue that it erases the specific human histories of colonialism and capitalism, and installs in their place a universalizing history of the human species that is a void of normative meaning as the natural history of the planet. Proposals for counter-terms abound, including "Capitalocene" and "Plantationocene", to more effectively name the forces that are responsible for today's crises. This talk traces the contours of this discussion to much earlier episodes in which constitutional questions of rights, responsibilities, and citizenship were tabled in debates around climate change that involved the normative status of carbon emissions. In the late 1980s, environmental and economic expertise served to underwrite an imaginary of carbon as ahistorical, the same everywhere no matter where or for what purpose it is emitted, and thus fit for trading on global markets in the post-Bretton Woods world. This flattening of carbon's history set up struggles that continued to play out for the three decades of climate politics that followed. Only with the 2015 Paris Agreement did a settlement emerge that reconnects, partially, the universal time of science with the historical time of human experience. Despite its long history and significant stakes, this struggle has received less scholarly attention than its younger cousin, the debate about the place of humans and their differentiated histories in the Anthropocene. Its reconstruction provides important insights for thinking about contemporary challenges to the recognition of persisting inequalities rooted in human histories of violence and difference.

Beyond the Citizen-Procedure-Outcomes Triangle: Co-production and the Making of Deliberative Democratic Theory *Hilton Simmet, Harvard Kennedy School*

In this paper I take up a problem of deliberative democratic theory (DDT) in the work of John Rawls, Jürgen Habermas and Hélène Landemore. I argue that at the heart of DDT is something of a paradox, one that gives the citizens the freedom to deliberate, while holding them to epistemic standards of being deliberate. These law-like constraints are what I call the "citizen-procedure-outcomes triangle": standards for who counts as a reasonable citizen (Rawls), what is a rational procedure (Habermas) and what are "smart" outcomes (Landemore). These rules hold politics up to a three-cornered epistemic standard that points toward theoretical ideals of "justice," "consensus" and "truth" against which politics can be evaluated as worthy or wanting. To critique these ideal epistemic constraints I turn to work in Science and Technology Studies (STS) that empirically examines how epistemic standards are embedded in social meanings and are products of political settlements. Sheila Jasanoff's concept of "co-production" illuminates how epistemic standards are made in ways that reflect modes of epistemic and political theorizing by political subjects in situ. I use this framework to revisit DDT and bring it into conversation with parallel strands of thinking in critical social science. To this end,

I look at the citizen-procedure-outcomes triangle in terms of making citizenship, making procedures and making public demonstrations.

Session Organizers:

Hilton Simmet, Harvard Kennedy School

Stefan Schäfer, Institute for Advanced Sustainability Studies

Karen Huang, Georgetown University

Chair:

Sheila Jasanoff, Harvard University

Discussant:

Ben Hurlbut, Arizona State University

460. Transparency and Algorithmic Governance - I: Legal and empirical examination of transparency and algorithmic governance

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

AI Transparency *Stefan Larsson, Lund University; Fredrik Heintz, Linköping University*

This conceptual paper revisits our published version of "transparency in artificial intelligence" (Internet Policy Review, 2020) in order to address the issues of transparency as linked to artificial intelligence (AI) from socio-legal and computer scientific perspectives. Firstly, we discuss the conceptual distinction between transparency in AI and algorithmic transparency, and argue for the wider concept "in AI", as a partly contested albeit useful notion in relation to transparency. Secondly, we show that transparency as a general concept is multifaceted, and of widespread theoretical use in multiple disciplines over time, particularly since the 1990s. Still, it has had a resurgence in contemporary notions of AI governance, such as in the multitude of recently published ethics guidelines on AI. Thirdly, we discuss and show the relevance of the fact that transparency expresses a conceptual metaphor of more general significance, linked to knowing, bringing positive connotations that may have normative effects to regulatory debates. Finally, we draw a possible categorisation of aspects related to transparency in AI, or what we interchangeably call AI transparency, and argue for the need of developing a multidisciplinary understanding, in order to contribute to the governance of AI as applied on markets and in society. Even if this is conceptual paper, there is a clear relevance for the legal STS area, that is, aspects of technological governance.

Algorithmic transparency and explainability for EU consumer protection: unwrapping the regulatory premises *Francesca Lagioia, Università di Bologna; Giovanni Sartor, University of Bologna; Agnieszka Jablonowska, European University Institute; Mateusz Grochowski, Max Planck Institute for International and Comparative Private Law*

The principles of transparency and explainability are guiding landmarks of the current EU regulatory policy towards artificial intelligence. Both are invoked in the policy guidelines as inspiring values that should govern algorithmic decision-making, while providing rationales for normative provisions – on information duties, access rights and control powers – established under the existing regulatory frameworks. This contribution delves into the debate on transparency and explainability from the EU consumer market perspective. First, the position of consumers relative to algorithmic decision-making is considered, and consumer risks concerning mass surveillance, exploitation, and manipulation are discussed. The concept of algorithmic opacity is analysed, distinguishing in particular technology-based opacity that is intrinsic to design choices, from relational opacity toward classes of users. The response of EU law to such problems is then considered. The emerging approach to algorithmic transparency (and explainability as a crucial aspect of

it) is connected to the broader and persisting regulatory goals concerning transparency in consumer markets. It is argued that EU law focuses on adequate information being provided to lay consumers (exoteric transparency), rather than on understandability to experts (exoteric transparency). A critical discussion follows on benefits of transparency to consumers, but also on its costs, and on the extent to which transparency can be implemented without affecting performance. Finally, the merits of a transparency-based regulation of algorithms are discussed and some general insights are provided on regulating transparency and explainability within the EU law paradigm.

Algorithmic Thinking: Taking a Cognitive Turn Towards Algorithmic Governance and Transparency *Aditya Johri, George Mason University; Ashish Hingle, George Mason University*

Within the conversation on algorithmic governance writ broadly, the notion of transparency has become a central idea.

Transparency allows one to better understand how precisely an algorithm drives outcomes. In this paper we approach this issue from a cognitive lens and argue that aligned closely with the issue of algorithmic governance is algorithmic thinking – what do we think of when we think of an algorithm and how do we think algorithms work? The conceptions we have of an algorithm are central to understanding how they can lend themselves to be transparent. We present an empirical approach to this issue and examine the perspectives of undergraduate computing and technology students, the future designers of both algorithms and systems, related to transparency. We use data from group discussions prompted by probes as well as dialogues that occur naturally in role-play scenarios discussions. The role-play scenario we use in our study is centered around the use of algorithms for lending. Our initial findings show that notions of transparency are strongly related with trust in the overall system and institution and on data and privacy. The notion of "function creep" in terms of what else can be done with the algorithm and how it can change over time is also important. An algorithm is not a stationary object or creation and therefore its transparency is also not a static characteristic. Students reported the difficulty of integrating micro-level applications issues with the larger macro-level societal issues of using this technology.

Cracking, Packing & Hijacking: Applying Machine Learning Tactics & Promoting Transparent Practices For Fair Political Maps *Marina Zafiris*

Redistricting is a complicated process that ultimately defines the political landscape of a state. While an increasing number of states employ independent commissions to draw district lines, in Texas, the legislature executes the decennial process of redrawing congressional and legislative lines, which will occur this year. Over time, these political maps have faced repeated legal challenges, due to allegations of racially discriminatory mapping that feed partisan agendas, giving certain political parties and voting groups unfair advantages or disadvantages. This controversial and unfair redistricting tactic is commonly known as gerrymandering. The Texas legislature's mapping practices, derived from census data and processed through Red Apple, a private software, remain undisclosed, which allow and promote gerrymandering. This paper serves as an investigation and applied case study of the undisclosed and biased political mapping practices conducted by the Texas Legislature, primarily dissecting their failure to uphold governance and accountability measures for their mapping methodologies. As we analytically sort through their selectively sequestered mapping pipeline, we dissect faults occurring within the following steps: data acquisition, processing, integration, modeling and validation. Additionally, we explore the potential benefits of open-source, machine learning based mapping practices to better generate realistic, representative and community-based districts that could be publicly and easily obtained and understood by the very

constituents these maps serve.

Session Organizer:

Jaakko Taipale, University of Helsinki

Chairs:

Susanna Lindroos-Hovinho, University of Helsinki

Jaakko Taipale, University of Helsinki

461. Splinternets - II: Infrastructures

8:00 to 9:30 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Participants:

National Politics, But Without the Fragmentation: What

"Splinternets" Miss *Nick Merrill*, *BioSENSE, UC Berkeley School of Information*

At the level of national politics (i.e., countries), discussions about the "splinternet" tend to center around one, core assumption: that Internet policies create internets that are different in different countries. For example, website blocking, when nation-states make particular websites unavailable within national borders, fragments the Internet: a particular website becomes accessible to some and not others. However, this description misses certain means by which national politics are enacted online. For example, website takedowns (e.g., seizing servers) are not fragmentation events: they make content equally unavailable for everyone. In this paper, I argue that discussions about "splinternets" *per se* elude certain methods of Internet control that manage to take a global effect---methods disproportionately used by the United States. (While the US does not block any websites, it also doesn't need to: the ICE-administered Operation In Our Sites has seized over a million webpages in its existence). This paper seeks a description of how national politics plays out via actions on the Internet; how national action can both fragment the Internet and unify it around a hegemonic (if unrestricted) set of norms and content, and how these strategies relate to political power and to ideological commitments.

The 'China Question' on Internet Fragmentation: Insights from Expert Interviews *Riccardo Nanni*

In its technically open, market-based, and multistakeholder dimensions, the Internet is possibly the 21st century's epitome of the Liberal International Order in its global spatial dimension. Therefore, many see the challenge of digital sovereignty and government-led fragmentation as representative of a broader tide of normative contestation of the Liberal International Order, both from its inside (populist movements) and from the outside (revisionist powers). According to many Western observers, China is nowadays' main agent of Internet fragmentation. This research analyses the potential for Chinese public and private stakeholders to act as Internet 'fragmenters' at the logical and economic and societal layers of digital governance. Analysis is based on qualitative expert interviews with Chinese and Western members of six Internet stakeholder communities (governments, international organisations, multinationals, civil society, academia, technical community), interpreted through a historical-institutionalist lens. By involving technologists in the analysis, this article borrows from STS scholarship to contribute to bridging a conceptual gap in International Relations scholarship, where the role of epistemic communities in governance processes is acknowledged but often overlooked in analysis. This article concludes that Chinese stakeholders have little to no interest in a technically fragmented Internet, as it would reduce scale economies in new Internet-enabled technologies' global market, running against the interest of China's and the world's major economic actors. However, the economic and societal layer remains at risk of fragmentation owing to different regulatory frameworks being adopted by public authorities, including China's 'Golden Shield'. Yet, whether or not this constitutes fragmentation is still open to debate.

The Relational Infrastructure of Cuban Splinternets

Michaelanne Thomas, School of Information at University of Michigan

Contrary to the common perception of a monolithic, global Internet, this paper focuses on multiple internet ecosystems, or splinternets, in Havana, Cuba. Similar to other states, such as China and Russia, the Cuban government has developed its own splinternet, CubaRed. However, state-sponsored versions of the Internet only account for part of the story. Against the backdrop of international media narratives that frame Cuba as an "isolated" country, I investigate the emergence of grassroots-driven internet ecosystems, such as a sneakernet maintained on USB thumb drives ("El Paquete") and an intranet custom-designed by citizens ("StreetNet"). Drawing on ethnographic research from 2014-2020, I demonstrate how limited but increasing access to the WWW interacts with Cuban-made internet ecosystems. I describe the roles that Habaneros occupy in the relational infrastructures. This work adopts a locally-situated perspective, highlighting the necessity of people and their relationships with one another internet ecosystems in a resource and politically-constrained environment. To understand splinternets and the future of the Internet, we must also understand the cultural ideologies and social roles that sustain internet ecosystems. I uncover the collective enterprises and negotiations that go towards the production of the Internet in Havana, thereby challenging established notions of what an (or the) Internet "should" look like in more and less connected contexts, as well as implications for how we understand the future of the WWW.

Session Organizer:

Elisa Oreglia, King's College London

Discussant:

Ashwin Jacob Mathew, King's College London

462. Interrogating "co-creation": the good, the bad, and the ugly - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Initiatives to stimulate innovation through "co-creation" among diverse actors are proliferating, whether driven from the top-down through governments and policy instruments (e.g. in living labs, public procurement of innovation and pre-commercial procurement) or bottom-up by business or civil society (e.g. in social innovation). But can and does co-creation (in its multiple configurations) really contribute to democratizing innovation, legitimizing interventions, addressing grand societal challenges, and facilitating sociotechnical transitions? How is co-creation enacted in practice? How do power asymmetries and incumbency shape co-creation outcomes? What are the possibilities and problems of efforts to scale-up co-creation across different locations? And how should we interrogate the practices, rhetoric, and normative implications of co-creation? In this panel, we interrogate the processes, practices, problems, publics and power structures surrounding the inflationary use of "co-creation" as remedy for innovation skepticism and democratic deficits — often combined with effort of up-scaling and replication its processes and results. We welcome empirical cases drawing on a variety of methods, analyses of co-creative practices that build on extant concepts in STS and neighboring fields, and new theoretical and conceptual developments. Comparative approaches across national boundaries, co-creation instruments, and technological domains and applications are more than welcome. We start the panel with an analysis of academic analyses of co-creation. The session continues examining co-creation practices in care, gerontology and energy transitions.

Participants:

What is co-production? Conceptualising and understanding 'co-production' across different theoretical perspectives *Justyna Bandola-Gill*, University of Edinburgh

'Co-production' is one of the key ideas in science-society relations— in terms of both its theoretical importance and its practical applications — being consistently discussed as the most

effective strategy for mobilising scientific knowledge in public. The concept of co-production was developed (almost) independently across multiple disciplines, including the public administration, STS and knowledge utilization and has been employed in various policy and practice fields such as environment/sustainability, health, and education. And yet, there is very little cross-disciplinary learning and debate regarding it. Co-production seems to be used as an umbrella term to encompass multiplicity of practical and theoretical approaches to science-policy/society interactions, including PPI, various deliberative fora, partnerships, etc. Consequently, 'co-production' is used to describe varying phenomena – from poststructuralist theories of the relationship between the science and the state to more utilitarian approaches to producing research impact. This paper will approach this set of issues by presenting a network analysis-driven review of the field of co-production. In particular, the paper will identify five predominant approaches to co-production as seen through the conceptual lenses of knowledge systems, knowledge democracy, 'new' science, boundary management and evidence use. These models are distinguished by their theoretical underpinnings, envisioned target groups and associated strategies.

The power of co-creation in the energy transformation - key conditions for co-creation in energy projects (Eastern European context) *Magdalena Rozwadowska, Wroclaw University of Economics and Business; Bozena Ryszawska, Wroclaw University of Economics*

Our paper concentrates on housing cooperatives' renewable energy projects and co-creation dynamics. The co-creation in energy transition is a relatively new field of research. We identify the co-creation process in Wroclaw Housing Cooperative and evaluate the relation between the top-down actions of Management Team and the bottom-up response of cooperative members. The primary data from interviews and questionnaires enable authors to discover and confirm success factors of the co-creation process and make recommendations for future projects. The DART model sets theoretical angle. The paper include a review of literature, case studies with a n aim to identify factors and international practices implemented by other organizations. The practical objective is to build recommendations for the entities/institutions that consider implementation projects using co-creation mechanisms. The conclusions of the research contribute to the scaling up co-creation activities in the process of creating climate neutrality of Europe.

Unpacking the meaning of “participatory engagement” within gerotechnology *Alisa Grigorovich, Brock University; Pia Kontos, KITE-Toronto Rehabilitation Institute, University Health Network; University of Toronto; Amanda Jenkins, Dalhousie University; Susan Kirkland, Dalhousie University*

Over the past decade, there has been a notable increase in research and advocacy efforts aimed at bringing about greater engagement of older adults in the co-creation and commercialization of technologies to support healthy aging and age-friendly products and services. Limited uptake and use of developed technologies, products, and services by older adults have prompted interest in participatory design and related approaches in the gerotechnology field. Despite this, recent systematic reviews suggest that contrary to key principles of participatory design, researchers often only engage older adults in providing advice or feedback in the early or later phases of gerotechnology research projects. A key barrier to more meaningful and active engagement of older adults in this field is the lack of understanding as to how participatory design differs from other participatory approaches, and in particular participatory action research. We address this gap in understanding by comparing and contrasting the theoretical similarities and differences between participatory design and participatory action research, using applied examples from

gerotechnology. We conclude with key barriers that are critical to address in order to achieve greater involvement of older adults in co-creation within gerotechnology, and to broaden and enrich the goals of this field.

Co-creating Oppression: 'Voice', Participation and Co-production in the Foster Care System *Kieran Cutting, Open Lab, Newcastle University; Lys Eden, Anglia Ruskin University*

In work with care-experienced young people in the UK, 'co-production' is becoming increasingly seen as 'best practice'. Yet best practice is malleable - it used to be best practice to ignore lived experience (in an attempt to appear objective), or to only seek out the 'voices' of care-experienced people in limited moments of consultation, prioritizing those voices which fit organizational narratives. The move towards co-production, then, should represent a significant shift in the power dynamics of service provision in the care system. What tends to happen, however, is that these previous ideas of best practice continue whilst masking themselves in the language of co-production, never meaningfully ceding any power. In this paper, we argue that despite any good intentions behind the rise of 'co-production', in practice it is too open to discursive manipulation by organizations and people in traditional positions of power. Co-production acts as a floating signifier to which any number of engagement practices (with varying levels of power) might be attached. Reflecting on our experiences, we suggest that co-production is primarily used to further commodify, fetishize and tokenize lived experiences. We describe how co-production might actually result in the reproduction of oppression and trauma through the constant retelling of harmful experiences and organizational efforts to frame these as static, objective truths. Instead, we suggest alternative practices which understand the importance of lived experience but which are critical of power and centered on giving those with lived experience the final say in the creation and provision of support services.

Session Organizer:

Carlos Cuevas-Garcia, Technical University of Munich

463. An Exquisite Corpse: Experiments in Practicing Better Relations as Scholars in Uncertain Times - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

The Exquisite Corpse (Le Cadavre Exquis, <https://www.artsy.net/article/artsy-editorial-explaining-exquisite-corpse-surrealist-drawing-game-die>) is a collaborative game of imperfect assemblage: each participant adds to a composition in sequence, not knowing or knowing little of what was added beforehand. In this panel, we deploy the “exquisite corpse” as a method and provocation for survival, collaboration, and playful relations during these uncertain times, investing not in fixed outcomes but emergent relationships and knowledges. We invite anyone interested in an imaginative and experimental exercise, and in forging a liminal space of collaboration and solidarity, to join us in collectively creating an exquisite corpse. Individual submissions should not be traditional conference presentations but stories, poems, visualizations, or other narrative forms that center around research spaces unsettled by disturbances, quakes, fires, waters, or human catastrophe; timelines, career trajectories, research plans, budgets or any project plan disrupted in the face of trauma and uncertainty; relationships and bodies broken, brittle, and precarious. The only condition is that you leave your contribution open to articulation, re-pair, and imaginative attachments that can ferment unsuspected forms of sense-making, relationship-building, knowledge-production, and negotiation. Collectively, we will then assemble and draw connections that create multiple possibilities and outcomes for a more careful academic practice. Through the configuration of this exquisite corpse, we will explore the folds, redirections, and emergent properties that can generate good relations within the university and beyond.

Participants:

Useful and Beautiful: Toward Reparative Knowledge

Organisation Techniques *Melissa Adler, Western University*

Eros, Oikos is a new collaborative project among library, archives, and museum workers who are also artists and poets. Our aim is to use art, story-telling, craft, and poetry to resist colonial, heteropatriarchal knowledge organization techniques by imagining, visualizing, and narrating a multitude of relations. Queer theorist Eve Kosofsky Sedgwick's reparative reading practices, textile artwork, and poetry provide models for reparative techniques. In particular, her "loom book" weaves textile and lines from Proust to express her own erotic identifications with literature. It enacts the "making and unmaking and remaking of and redissolution of hundreds of old and new categorical imaginings" (1990, 23). As the organizer of Eros, Oikos, I will bring the artists and writers who are participating in the project into dialogue with Sedgwick, as well as the first century Greek historian and miscellanist Pamphila, whose method for organising information was associated with the concept of poikilia. She recorded the stories that she heard in her household in the order in which they came to her, rather than organizing them by subject, so as to please the reader. Her histories were regarded as useful and beautiful. Anne Carson (2009, 357) offers an expansive definition for poikilia: "many-colored, spotted, dappled, variegated, intricate, embroidered, inlaid, highly wrought, complicated, changeful, diverse, abstruse, ambiguous, subtle." The aesthetics of poikilia privileges diversity and togetherness over uniformity and separateness. I will talk about the ways that Pamphila's and Sedgwick's techniques are useful for imagining knowledge organization techniques that foreground queer kinship, desire, and repair.

Umbrella Έλα 0.3 - "Non-" "Benevolence and Efficacy" *CHEN HUANG, City University of Hong Kong; Michael Leung, School of Creative Media*

A group of PhD researchers selected a phrase or word(s) that necessitated (re)definition in their own projects. Using these as a springboard for sharing specific situated concepts, how might entanglement and support between diverse areas of knowledge production be uncovered by staying open to emergent relations? Is a non- a "深圳人 (Shenzheners) a 本地人 (local) or an 外地人 (outsider), who or what has agency of (re)cognizing recognition, enacting benevolence and efficacy, where are proximity and situation located, isn't isn't everything a STORY?! At Wang Chau Village, where 500 non-indigenous villagers are currently being evicted, what do they think about this prefix? A couple of years ago I had a dream that I spoke to former Legislative Councillor Eddie Chu Hoi-dick about this prefix, and how adopting such words perpetuates the oppression of Wang Chau villagers, or at least builds a consciousness towards being displaced—contributing to a lack of solidarity from the public. Today in Hong Kong, there are currently 21 villages planned for eviction by the government. Upon the original of 1406, at least six successive editions of the famine herbal were published in major cities across the empire during the Ming. Divergent opinions on the principles of famine relief emerged from the prefaces of different editions: some diligent magistrates sponsored the reprint as a pragmatic solution of current famines, even with extra efforts to tailor it for local usage; some believed the dissemination of the famine herbal could be a backup of the established relief practices, or at least a gesture of benevolence, although living the people on their own were not morally and politically correct; there was also criticism on exaggerated significance of this book, suggesting that an over expectation on the "shelf-reliance" of the commoners would result in slack official performance in famine administration.

Interdisciplinary teaching tied through difference into communities of care *Sandra Patricia Gonzalez-Santos, Universidad Anahuac*

How can we connect with the other, that other who we have been told to see as different, unapproachable, incomprehensible, who's

appearance has been highlighted over everything else? [Flashback to my 4 year-old self watching Sesame Street's game "three of these things belong together" where you had to identify the one that was different because it was "doing its own thing". Were those moments when we were being taught that the similar go together and the different are to be separated?] ¿Cómo conectar desde la diferencia? How to communicate with, generate empathy with, work together with a person how has a different life story, whose vulnerabilities and privileges are different, who holds different beliefs and knowledges, and who speak other languages (sometimes disciplinary other times cultural or ethnic). How to work from / with difference? To explore, experiment and think about this, I turn to teaching. Having had the opportunity of simultaneously teaching in different contexts, working with interdisciplinary research groups, under-graduate and post-graduate students as a coordinator, a teacher, a tutor and a supervisor, I have been made aware that there are strategies (mostly inspired in feminist STS) one can use to make these experiences become communities of care. Communities where we learn and put into practice other ways of being human. Communities where the strings that tie and make work possible are drawn from the skein of difference. In this presentation I share five strategies I have found useful: Implosion 2.0 (a take on Joe Dumit's 2014 paper), el acitrón (Sánchez-Aguilar & González-Santos, 2019), care-full questioning (González-Santos & Boltvinik, 2018), collaborative teaching, arts based teaching methods.

Umbrella Έλα 0.3: Proximity & Situation *Kay Mei Ling Beadman; Riar Rizaldi, City University of Hong Kong*

A group of PhD researchers selected a phrase or word(s) that necessitated (re)definition in their own projects. Using these as a springboard for sharing specific situated concepts, how might entanglement and support between diverse areas of knowledge production be uncovered by staying open to emergent relations? Is a non- a "深圳人 (Shenzheners) a 本地人 (local) or an 外地人 (outsider), who or what has agency of (re)cognizing recognition, enacting benevolence and efficacy, where are proximity and situation located, isn't everything a STORY?! Chinese philosopher Kang You-wei's Datong Shu is a century old, utopian treatise with eugenic ideas at its core. A super race of Chinese and white mixedness is proposed, which would take "a millennia and several hundred years" to achieve. Proximity Veil is a speculative fiction response, set in a future in which facial feature obscuration can be turned on at the flick of an implant switch. How might speculative stories provide a means to unsettle time and in so doing open up spaces to illuminate complex current understandings of mixed race identity formation and societal assumptions now? Based on the detoured psychogeographical research developed by the Situationists, the practice of psychogeophysics, as theorised in this study of massively mined Bangka island in Indonesia, is an effort to reflect the networks of social elements, economic force, and geophysical transformation in order to imagine a situation where collective relations can emerge in a new social order. The speculation of creating the situation is conditioned through interactions obtained directly on the island, not only with traditional anthropological approaches, through ethnography and fieldwork, but also by a series of encounters with mining technology, geological formation and earth strata, as well as ideas generated by the inhabitants in relation to their understanding of value and material.

The 'good' academic in unsettled times *Sarah R Davies, University of Vienna*

The figure of the 'good academic' has been subject to sustained critique: in many academic evaluation regimes, goodness equates to problematic and exclusionary notions of 'excellence', internationality, and productivity (Lund 2015; Thornton 2014). In this contribution I wish to re-think the question of how to be a good academic, and to reclaim goodness as a potential practice of

care, vulnerability, generosity, and solidarity. My aim is to collaborate with others to explore the forms that goodness might take in the context of diverse situations, career stages, and bodies, to resist and subvert mainstream forms of academic evaluation, and to craft experimental answers to the question: how should the good academic be? I raise these issues by drawing on an auto-ethnography of digital academic practice in the pandemic, mobilising images, ethnographic vignettes, screenshots and other ephemera as a starting point for reflection and a provocation as to what could and should be otherwise. These snapshots are disjointed and non-linear, rejecting tidy narratives or arguments; instead, they offer the possibility of connection, re-assembly, transformation, or attachment. In offering them up as one limb of the exquisite corpse, my hope is to engage in the collective production of new meanings, possibilities, and relations for a good academic life.

Session Organizers:

Jade Vu Henry, Goldsmiths, University of London

Lisa Lehner, Cornell University

Nadine Tanio, University of California, Irvine

464. Inclusion and Its Consequences: The Politics of Diversity and Recognition in Health Data Projects - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Engaging with the 4S 2021 conference theme, this panel explores the practices and consequences of data inclusion and exclusion in unequal worlds. We welcome empirical and conceptual papers examining health data projects of various scales, that consider some of the following questions: What are the various promises of diversity linked to data projects and how do these promises shape inclusion and exclusion practices, efforts, and outcomes? What are the tradeoffs and dilemmas inherent in and arising from narratives and practices of inclusion in health data projects? What are the drivers of activism around inclusion in health data and, alternatively, what drives resistance? How do current struggles for inclusion in health data today differ from demands for inclusion in the past? What sorts of visibilities and erasures might inclusion and exclusion in health data produce? This panel invites papers examining data assemblages and what it means to be counted (or not) in health data, to whom, and for what ends. Papers might address, for example, the inclusion or exclusion of various identifiers and statuses in state surveillance systems, the participation or refusal of communities in health data repositories, interrogations of public and private institutions that seek to obscure data collection, and erasures and ethical challenges that arise as data emerge from and circulate across geographic scales from the local to the transnational.

Participants:

Public Engagement around Genetic Data Controversies:

Balancing Respect for Persons and the Common Good *Ilaria Galasso*, University College Dublin; *Susi Geiger*, University College Dublin

Henrietta Lacks' "immortal cells" have been invaluablely beneficial for studying and developing treatments around a variety of human diseases. But her data were used and published with no consent from her or any family member (Skloot 2010). In this paper we contrast communitarian "duty to share" and libertarian "self-ownership" in the context of genetics research: we scrutinize the route to justice when the imperative of (diverse) inclusion for the common good is in conflict with respect for persons, especially when vulnerable categories are at stake, such as patients or underserved populations. We analyzed two contemporary controversies by following the debates on (social) media and by interviewing concerned actors: the case of the Wellcome Sanger Institute accused to unauthorizedly commercialize African DNA samples (<https://www.sciencemag.org/news/2019/10/major-uk-genetics-lab-accused-misusing-african-dna>), and the case of Genuity Science's opt-out approach to genetic research with brain tumor

samples in Ireland (<https://www.thejournal.ie/selling-our-genes-5219781-Oct2020/>). Two aspects emerged as critical: trust misuse and asymmetry in research leadership. We interpret our findings in the context of participatory science (Callon et al. 2001, Bucchi and Neresini 2008) and of engagement in medical research (Solomon et al. 2016) as a way to co-produce research by negotiating and reconciling interests: we propose a participatory framework in which publics are actively engaged in genetics research, and we engage with the concerned actors ourselves in the first place, as STS scholars, by grounding our research on their voices as expressed in the interviews, and exploring and possibly initiating with them spaces where they can meaningfully voice their interests.

The Racial Politics of Data Diversity *Anna Jabloner*, Harvard University; *Alexis Walker*, Columbia University

A pair of pie-charts – highlighting the overwhelming European ancestry of participants in genomic studies worldwide – have become the de-facto visual representation of a widespread concern amongst geneticists and scholars of genomics in society. The argument that "Genomics is failing on diversity," as the title of that 2016 Nature paper stressed, has permeated discussions in academic and private sector research. This talk presents data from interview and survey research in commercial genomics, where participants cite these diversity issues as the most pressing ethics concern in their industry today. Ensuing efforts to diversify genomic data often represent projects toward improving the healthcare of Black and indigenous Americans, who have historically been victims of a structurally racist U.S. health system. In practice, however, we show how calls to diversify genomic data often morph into calls to get more Black and Brown people into databases, and people of color are aggressively lobbied to give their data, lest they block progress for their own communities. Taking up the conference's call to interrogate data in- and exclusions, we tackle this corollary phenomenon as pushes for data diversity get articulated within larger U.S. racial politics. We ask: 1) as diverse data in the private sector bring economic benefits, could more distributive participant compensation models create more meaningful modes of justice? 2) Since demands to diversify genomic databases can reproduce ingrained American ideas of genetic race, can we think beyond the inclusion of samples from different bodies in health data projects toward other justice trajectories?

Data Politics in Precision Medicine Research: Reflections on the Promise of Inclusion from Investigators and Frontline Staff *Emily Vasquez*, Columbia University; *Stephanie Malia Fullerton*, University of Washington; *Aliya Saperstein*, Stanford University; *Michael Bentz*, Columbia University; *Nicole Foti*, University of California, San Francisco; *Sandra Soo-Jin Lee*, Columbia University

Drawing on ethnographic research conducted across three precision medicine research (PMR) consortia in the United States, this paper analyzes how investigators and frontline staff reflect on the problematic allure of "Big Data" projects and the questionable value of data drawn from diverse communities to resolve local health disparities. Discussions with PMR investigators and frontline study staff elucidate emergent tensions including: The strengths and limitations of precision medicine datasets currently under construction, the production of additional data in the absence of tangible on-the-ground action to promote health, and how to justify their own role within big data projects in the domain of precision medicine. Recognition of these scientists' critical reflections on their own work in precision medicine research initiatives is essential as PMR initiatives strive to involve diverse participants from historically underrepresented groups and increasingly target socioeconomically vulnerable communities for recruitment. Reflections from investigators and frontline staff also contribute to theoretical conversations in STS attending to datafication, its

drivers and its consequences, highlighting both technical and social factors underpinning the ongoing datafication of health and health disparities.

Postmortem Inequalities: Social and Spatial Disparity in National Mortality Surveillance Data *Katherine Michele Tote, University at Albany, SUNY*

In the United States, depending on where you die, your cause of death is first recorded by a physician, a coroner, or a medical examiner. This record is forwarded by your local health department to the “oldest and most successful” example of inter-governmental data sharing, the National Vital Statistics System (NVSS). Your cause of death is transformed into an ICD-10 code, and you are then semi-anonymously immortalized in the NVSS Multiple Cause of Death Microdata file, where your demographic characteristics, county and date of death, and the codes that summarize the reason behind your demise are available to any researcher who submits a data request. The analysis and interpretation of these data often has tangible public consequences, but the process is not always transparent. How do we count cause-specific mortality? Who is (un)intentionally excluded, and why? How are these data used, and how can we ensure that the portraits we paint of disease landscapes approximate reality? From regional differences in death ascertainment processes to racial disparities in post-mortem toxicology screenings, biases in mortality data can obfuscate public health crises and misdirect harm reduction or disaster relief -- the implications of disparate data quality and completeness have been illuminated in the wake of America’s recent COVID-19 and opioid epidemics. This paper examines the (in)completeness of national mortality records and the various moments where ‘silence’ (Trouillot 1995) can enter the process of data collection and interpretation, and additionally explores how we can mitigate biases introduced by missing data beyond traditional quantitative methods.

Session Organizers:

Janet K. Shim, University of California, San Francisco
Sandra Soo-Jin Lee, Columbia University

465. Beyond Solutionism for a Responsible Artificial Intelligence - II: Production & Pragmatic Approaches

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

We propose a post-solutionist reflection on what is Responsible AI, to discuss interdisciplinary perspectives that contribute to making AI systems more fair, transparent, and inclusive. Solutionism is “recasting all complex social situations either as neat problems with definite, computable solutions or as transparent and self-evident processes that can be easily optimized if only the right algorithms are in place!” (Morozov 2013) Ethical problems in AI/ML have been exposed through numerous and influential publications (Buolamwini & Gebu 2018, Challen & al 2019, Parikh & al 2019, Yapo & Weiss 2018). How can we move from a view of ethics and responsibility narrowly focused on technical definitions of bias, discrimination, and fairness in AI systems to one which considers interconnecting issues of cognitive bias, social inequality, white supremacy, intersectionality, geopolitical and economic divides? A robust consideration of ethics and responsibility requires that we interrogate how technologies are interwoven with our social structures, histories, and moral imaginations (Noble 2018; Benjamin 2019). We must go beyond tech solutionism to frame problems without automatically assuming AI/ML is the best or inevitable course of action, to fully explore fine-grain signals and our complete range of options, which can include refusal. Topics to be addressed in this session include power and ubiquity of automated systems in daily life, over-trust in technical solutions, and whether our current production methodologies support or hinder just and equitable AI systems.

Participants:

Can Workers Hold AI Accountable?: A Typology of Collective Action, 2010 to 2020 *Nataliya Nedzhvetskaya, University of California, Berkeley; JS Tan*

States, corporations, and international governing organizations are recognized as powerful actors in the field of AI ethics and governance. The role of AI workers, whose labor builds and trains algorithms, remains largely under theorized by contrast. We introduce a typology of worker collective actions in AI through an analysis of the Collective Action in Tech archive (<https://data.collectiveaction.tech/>). Actions in the “AI Applications” category challenge AI technologies in practice. These actions criticize (a) general AI applications when methods are relevant to a larger professional community or (b) narrow AI applications when processes are limited to a single organization. Actions in the “AI Working Conditions” category criticize the labor conditions of AI workers. These actions condemn (c) algorithmic oppression when algorithms are directly responsible for exploitation or (d) adjacent inequalities when structural violence on the basis of employment status, race, gender, or other markers threatens survival in the AI workplace. AI workers play a unique role in holding AI accountable. Capitalist competition leads to value erosion in the application of AI, and corporate governance organizations are unfit to mitigate this because their function is to legitimate corporate power. AI workers often demand accountability on issues that threaten to delegitimize their employers. Through discourse analysis of workers’ open letters, and petitions, and websites, we demonstrate how AI workers in each of these four categories adopt distinctly different strategies to make their claims.

Humanising data work: Towards responsible machine intelligence *Bidisha Chaudhuri, International Institute of Information Technology Bangalore; Sravya C, IIT Bangalore*

From facial recognition to social media platforms to voice-based assistants, most advanced algorithmic systems are fueled by vast datasets to make predictions, recommendations or automate various tasks. The datasets required by these systems need to be cleaned, labelled, and verified - all of which is dependent on human effort (Bilić, 2016; Irani & Silberman, 2013). The tech industry invisibilises this human effort by foregrounding its algorithmic capabilities in ways that hide the data-tasks necessary to build, train and support the algorithms (Irani, 2015; Gray & Suri, 2019). The language of “cutting-edge innovation”, advanced computation and “data-driven solutions” masks the human labour necessary to gather, sanitize, and verify data and configure, and adjust machines and models to use data. Even within the AI/ML developer community, model building work is more desirable and viewed in higher esteem than data work (Sambasivan et al, 2021). Drawing on existing literature on displacement of labour in the global data-driven economy (Irani 2015, Bilić 2016, Crain, Poster & Cherry 2016, Gray & Suri 2019, Ekbia & Nardi 2017) we critically examine the trajectories of skills, expertise and career aspirations among data labelling workers through a qualitative case study in India. By rendering the data labelling work and workers visible, we call for expanding the discourse on responsible AI to reflect on the invisibilization of data work, how it deepens the faultlines of geopolitical and economic divides, and engage with the needs, desires and aspirations of data workers.

Epistemic Instability During AI Design: The Limitations Of Designers’ Interpretations *Jonne Maas, Delft University of Technology*

An AI system is often assessed by its epistemic value, expressed in terms of the accuracy of the system’s output and the output’s robustness regarding contextual changes. Yet, before we can analyse the epistemic value of a system, we must first understand how the design of said system constitutes its output and, by doing so, restricts its epistemic potential. In other words, I want to ask how the epistemic instability during a system’s design phase affects the system’s final output, and what role does a designer play in this? I call epistemic inability the yet-to-be-defined

options during the design phase. For instance, as part of my PhD research which started in November 2020, I investigate a system that incorporates ambiguous terms like ‘inequality’ and ‘democracy’. These terms require a concrete definition, forcing the programmer to choose which understanding of these terms are most suitable for the envisaged purpose of the program. There is hence an epistemic instable phase during the design process where it is unclear which definition of a term will be used. This phase is overcome once the designers concretely define these terms. From this point on, the term becomes “fossilised” and there are no further possible interpretations. Such fossilization influences the epistemic potential of the system: although the system’s epistemic value may be great in terms of accuracy, its value is grounded in the situated knowledge of the designer, thereby restricting the epistemic potential of the system. This contributes to the power of AI designers.

Session Organizer:

Frederique Krupa, DIGITAL Design Lab, l'école de design Nantes Atlantique

Chair:

Sarah Luger, Orange Silicon Valley

Discussant:

Katherine Fletcher, OpenStax at Rice University

466. Building a new heuristic: knowledge production processes in interaction I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Participants:

Actores sociales y diálogo de saberes en el proceso de producción de conocimiento *Melisa Cuschnir*

En el año 2012 se presentó en Argentina un nuevo instrumento de política científica impulsado por el Ministerio de Ciencia Tecnología e Innovación Productiva: los Proyectos de Desarrollo Tecnológico y Social (PDTs). Estos proyectos de investigación nacen bajo el propósito de promover tecnologías asociadas a la resolución de una problemática social específica o al aprovechamiento de una oportunidad estratégica del mercado, generando una vinculación directa y necesaria con sujetos e instituciones demandantes de dichos conocimientos. De esta forma se incorporan y reconocen de manera formal a actores sociales como participantes necesarios del proceso investigativo. Esta ponencia tiene por objetivo compartir los resultados de mi tesis de maestría, en la cual propongo analizar quiénes son, en qué forma y bajo qué propósitos y circunstancia participan diferentes actores sociales de los PDTs como parte del proceso de investigación. A partir de recuperar la voz y la experiencia de los actores sociales, se analizan los sentidos que le atribuyen a su participación, a la toma de decisión, al diálogo entre saberes y conocimientos puestos en circulación. En este marco se busca indagar acerca de las interacciones entre equipos de investigación y actores sociales, como también en los vínculos entre la universidad, la ciencia y su entorno. La metodología se basa en un análisis cualitativo, asumiendo un diseño de investigación flexible. El trabajo se enmarca en un estudio de casos múltiples, en la cual fueron seleccionados proyectos iniciados entre 2012 y 2018 de distintas áreas disciplinares dentro del banco de datos de PDTs.

A model of social appropriation of STI to promote research agendas in Mexico’s National Healthcare System: analyzing the mobilization of knowledge DM2 researchers *Juan Carlos García Cruz, Cátedras CONACYT/ UAM Xochimilco*

The literature on processes concerning the transfer, mobilization, and appropriation of knowledge produced in universities and public research centers has provided results that allow us to better understand the benefits, obstacles, determinant and knowledge

channels of such processes. Within such literature, however, the emphasis has been placed on the differences among researchers, other agents and institutions instead of attempting to understand the epistemic practices that affect the mobilization of knowledge. Thus, there are still theoretical and empirical lack of knowledge regarding the processes concerning the social appropriation of science, technology and innovation (STI), for instance: how artifacts and other technologies can be altered by users with the capacity to promote meaningful changes, or how knowledge may be mobilized within research groups in order to make contributions to the scientific community and society in general. In this sense, the question is: What are the characteristics of knowledge mobilization of DM2 researchers and how do these characteristics impact or benefit other areas? In specific the main objective is To identify the mobilization of knowledge of researchers in Type 2 Diabetes and their interaction with other sectors to develop a model of social appropriation of ST&I.

Assembling The Collaboration-Puzzle: Integrating Dispersed Knowledge On Individual-Level Antecedents For Scientific Collaborations With Non-Professional Scientists *Susanne Beck, LBG OIS Center & Copenhagen Business School; Agnes Effert, LBG Open Innovation in Science Center; Olga Kokshagina, RMIT University; Karin Hoisl, University of Mannheim; Marion Poetz, Copenhagen Business School*

Across disciplines, the production of scientific knowledge increasingly involves collaboration and co-creation with individuals not primarily employed in the academic science system (e.g., patients, indigenous people, managers). Such collaborations are claimed to yield promising benefits for science (e.g., more novel research) and for society (e.g., democratization of science). Yet, the discussions about antecedents for successful collaborations remain within the respective disciplinary boundaries, creating dispersed piles of valuable but disconnected insights due to many idiosyncrasies in terms of languages used, stakeholders involved, and forms of collaborations applied and investigated. This hampers the development of an integrated, cross-disciplinary understanding of successful collaborations. Our integrative review addresses this challenge by focusing on an often-presumed and diverse source of collaboration success—the individuals involved—and classifying collaborations along three theory-grounded, unifying dimensions: collaborators’ field proximity, number of different stakeholder groups involved, and their participation in professional vs. personal roles. We systematically reviewed 33,216 papers retrieved through a keyword search in Scopus and EBSCOhost across all disciplines, out of which 78 met the criteria of testing, proposing, or reflecting upon individual-level antecedents for scientific collaborations. Our analysis reveals 103 individual-level factors in 19 categories influencing three outcome dimensions: initial propensity to engage in collaborations, collaborators behavior, and (perceived) collaboration success. The resulting integrative framework further distinguishes between individual-level drivers of and barriers for scientists and non-professional scientists as well as those resulting from their interaction. Our findings contribute to the configuration of a new heuristic for collaborative knowledge production processes and the organization of science.

Building situated knowledge agendas: experiences from the University of the Republic in Uruguay *maria goñi, Universidad de la República (Uruguay); Camila Zeballos, Universidad de la República; Mariela Bianco Bozzo, Universidad de la República*

Production of knowledge in interaction among various actors reflects a trajectory of social commitment of public Latin American universities. This article focuses on the characteristics that the participation of non-academic actors has within knowledge production processes in interaction. The guiding question aims to identify the roles non-academic actors acquire

when they engage in knowledge processes with academic actors. For this purpose, a set of projects funded by the Research Program Oriented to Social Inclusion of the University of the Republic in Uruguay is taken as an empirical reference. The participation of non-academic actors is examined on the basis of three specific dimensions (profiles, communication flow, and intervention) that contribute to the construction of knowledge processes in a gradient from collaboration to co-production. In terms of ideal types, collaboration and co-production simplify the heterogeneity of possible relationships between "experts and laymen" when situated knowledge agendas are fostered.

Session Organizer:

Camila Zeballos, Universidad de la Republica

467. Caste as/of Technoscience - IV

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Despite its continued importance as an analytical category in the social life of south asia, and south asians globally, caste as a lens or a category of analysis has historically remained relatively undertheorized in the social studies of science and technology. If at all, caste has largely figured as an identity category in extant work. Can reframing the study of caste as a study of technoscience improve our engagements with caste as a social category as well as that of the social study of science and technology? What conceptual and methodological toolkit would such a move need? How are caste and technoscience intertwined? Is caste an historically morphing assemblage which shapeshifts as new sociotechnical arrangements become possible/are enabled by it? If so, what new ways of thinking about caste are enabled when we approach 'caste' as technoscience? And vice versa, what new ways of thinking about technoscience are enabled as we think about 'technoscience' as caste? This panel invites papers that work with caste not only in axes of identity vis a vis technoscientific worlds but also think through caste as technoscience. These may range from case studies of sociotechnical assemblages that converge around different kinds of "work," debates around labour and caste relations, discursive efforts towards castelessness in the name of "merit," to theoretical pieces that reflect on methodological concerns on the matter which address the co-construction and reification of the caste system through technoscientific practices, imagination and rhetoric in different communities of South Asia and its diaspora.

Participants:

Caste Mobilities In Rurban Technoscapes: Examining Flashlights, Wedding Processions And DJ Trucks *Gayas Eapen*, North Carolina State University

This paper explores how caste symbiotically evolves, reifies and gets undermined in relation to technoscientific objects and infrastructure. For this presentation, I focus on three objects that are embedded in relations of caste and mobility in modern India. The first object, flashlights (or torches as they're called in India), are often workarounds to unequal electrification infrastructures. As anthropologist Jamie Cross points out, electrical distribution networks are implicated in caste hierarchies, particularly in rural India owing to physical and geographic segregation (Cross, 2019). Not needing to negotiate bureaucratic and local power hierarchies, flashlight brings about an encounter with modernity that temporarily weakens the "upper" caste stronghold on essential infrastructures. However, they also evince new relations with mobility, illumination and justice that are far from ideal. Wedding processions, my second object, instantiates how stable infrastructures — streets and locales in this case— interact with an assemblage of mobile objects including bodies, lights, horses, musical instruments among others. The frequent attacks on Dalits (historically marginalized within the "lower" castes) when their wedding processions pass through "upper" caste locales or streets thus sustain the spatial boundaries of caste, despite modern infrastructural imaginaries of the nation. The third object, DJ trucks, illustrates the interaction between automobility and sonic spaces. DJ trucks lay claim to space through loud music bordering on sensorial violence, alongside the visual bravado of a

repurposed truck. However, they accentuate competitive sonic exchanges (Matzner, 2012) that have a lineage in revivalist "upper" caste Hindu nationalist projects combining sound and mobility (Manuel, 1993).

Sounding out caste *Vebhuti Duggal*

It is well-established that the late nineteenth and early twentieth century media and infrastructures transformed soundscapes, regimes of sense perception, bodily habitations and techniques, globally. For India and South Asia, these transformations were part of the colonial encounter and crucially, also implicated caste. Caste, then, marks both technology and sound (whether musical or non-musical) in India and South Asia. Accordingly, this paper proposes considering the questions of caste, sound and technology by focusing on collective listening by looking at a selection of archival material across the long twentieth century colonial administration records and one English language newspaper. It excavates caste in writing about sound technologies such as the radio, loudspeaker, and gramophone. This paper asks thus, the questions of technics: what does it mean to 'hear' caste? How do normative caste-based listening practices consolidate over time? What does technology, especially sound technology, do to questions of caste?

When caste networks meet mobile networks: an ethnographic study of the relationship between communication technology and caste *Murali Shanmugavelan*

The power of ubiquitous mobile phones has led to the assertion of their roles in toppling governments, organising social movements, diversifying livelihood opportunities and empowering marginalised communities, including Dalits. This presentation offers a critical update of this view through a combination of an ethnographic study of a Dalit caste group in Tamil Nadu and a systematic literature review of caste, mobile phone and technology studies. This presentation will focus on the role of the everyday use of mobile phones in the lives of Arunthathiyars – one of the most oppressed caste groups in Tamil Dalit category – when negotiating with the dominant caste group to live by the side with dignity and without fear. It further employs three caste-oriented communication analytics, such as articulation, spaces and silence (Shanmugavelan 2019), to analyse the everyday use of mobile phones by Arunthathiyars. In particular, the presentation will focus on the constant power play between caste networks and mobile networks. The presentation will critically appraise the notion that mobile phones are enablers of social networks that connect human/s with the outer world, a notion that is common in the field of communication studies. Instead, the presentation will show the use of mobile phone networks in the kudiyruppu (a Dalit colony) is a tool to keep Arunthathiyars' space insular, protected and intact. Reference Shanmugavelan, M. (2018). Everyday Communicative Practices of Arunthathiyars: The Contribution of Communication Studies to the Analysis of Caste Exclusion and Subordination of a Dalit Community in Tamil Nadu, India [Doctoral Dissertation], SOAS University of London.

Session Organizer:

Palashi Vaghela, Cornell University

Discussant:

Deepak Prince, GITAM University, Hyderabad

468. Climate change and the governance of time - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Participants:

Intersecting Climate Change: Temporal Reorientations In The German Forest *Asher Boersma*, Universität Konstanz

This paper reports on ongoing ethnographic fieldwork in a German biosphere reserve—a bureaucratic entity which aims for social and ecological sustainability in a particular area. As such,

it covers a great variety of phenomena: biodiversity, tourism, education, agriculture, to name a few. Though these all come with different, often entangled temporalities, one intersects them all: climate change. Central to this paper is the forest. The German Forest has been a prominent cultural trope since the nineteenth century. Recently, press reports that forests in Germany are in steep decline due to climate change have increased. Although climate is the long-term average of weather conditions in a particular area, and as such not observable as concrete event, media outlets can now represent vistas of dead pine trees. Climate change has always depended on media to be registered: it is a spatio-temporally distributed phenomenon and is contingent on media to be seen. However, now climate change materialises, albeit indirectly, through other phenomena it causes: through extreme weather it causes an event, through the loss of biodiversity, on which the forest as ecosystem relies for survival, it becomes local. This asks temporal reorientations of many actors, which this paper details. The forester, for instance, is trained to think a timespan of 150 years, but now faces acute challenges. Although most established solutions are long-term, they clash with public expectations of a timeless and stable forest, which in the form of tourism translate into short term commercial dependencies.

Rhythms in Transition: Engaging Rhythmanalysis with Energy-Climate Relations *gordon Walker*

In this paper, I bring the concepts and tools of rhythmanalysis to bear on the multiple temporalities of climate change and the transitions in rhythms and rhythmic relations that are intrinsic to stripping carbon out of everyday energy dependencies. In the foundational rhythmanalytic writing of Lefebvre and Regulier, energy is positioned centre stage in defining what rhythm is, but little engagement has followed in subsequent scholarship. Drawing on a recently published monograph, I propose a newly energised multidisciplinary and materialist rhythmanalysis, which follows the beats and pulses of energy flows in everyday life in order to open up the polyrhythmic interweaving of the techno-energy of energy systems, with the energetic exchanges of planetary movements, environmental and bodily processes. Traditional energy systems are cast as vast rhythmically constituted assemblages drawing carbon resources into the coordinated rhythms of commodification, combustion and consumption, with increasingly arrhythmic impacts on the expected repetitions of climate and environment. It is argued that the governance of multi-sited transitions in rhythms needs to be made more visible in the materialisation of temporally recalibrated and de-carbonised energy infrastructures.

The ethics of climate adaptation *Neelke Doorn, Professor; Lieke Brackel, Delft University of Technology; Sara Vermeulen, TU Delft, Department of Values, Technology and Innovation; Udo Pesch, Delft University of Technology*

It is now widely accepted that climate change requires adaptation measures to cope with its effects, such as increased droughts, heat waves, and flooding. These measures prompt important ethical questions. First, climate adaptation policies establish a role division in terms of who has to do what, with that settling questions about which parties are included and excluded, which parties are beneficiaries, victimized and forgotten. As such, these policies confront us with strong queries about social justice and responsibility, necessitating critical reflection. Second, addressing the different effects of climate change may require conflicting interventions. For example, strategies to prevent flooding may conflict with drought strategies or ecological objectives. This prompts questions about how to reconcile or prioritize these different interventions and which claims to acknowledge. Third, addressing issues of climate change involves a long term planning orientation taking place at different territorial scales. This may shift the focus away from the everyday environmental justice struggles that local communities are currently struggling with. In many cases, these moral issues

are neglected because of the techno-centric nature with which climate adaptation is approached. Our paper will address the question how to engage with these moral questions. In this we will look at the issues listed above, and connect these to the role of dominant conceptions of natural and administrative boundaries in climate adaptation policy. These boundaries are decisive because climate change issues transcend geographical, administrative, and temporal scales, while policy demand the construction of unequivocal boundaries.

The Governance of Time through Modelling: Uncertainty as Argumentative Time-Work in Denialist Discourses of Climate Change *Alexandra Ciocanel, University of Bucharest; Mihai Dima, University of Bucharest*

If the scientific consensus on human-induced climate change is irrefutable, this is mainly a consensus on greenhouse gas emissions changing the climate in addition to natural variability. There is still an ongoing scientific debate on the tempo and mode of future modifications. Predicting how fast and in what manner change will happen still raises new questions for climate scientists. In this paper, we discuss how and why the uncertainty of scientific models for predicting future climate change becomes a resource for argumentative time-work (Ciocanel, Rughiniș, Flaherty 2020; Flaherty 2003) in contrarian views, aiming to completely discredit the science of climate change. A peer-reviewed paper published in *Climate Research* (Soon et. al 2001) drew attention to some of the deficiencies of climate change modelling, without refuting the anthropogenic causes of climate change. It has nonetheless entered in public circulation, being used by contrarian voices as a legitimation resource for undermining the science of climate change. Through following the circulation of this scientific paper in denialists arguments across multiple climate-skeptical platforms, we explore the assumptions about science and the future behind public understandings of scientific models and the different governances of time that they imply. We argue that scientific models might fail to be seductive beyond scientific arenas when there is a misalignment between what Pierre Bourdieu has identified as the specific temporalities of the logic of practice, and the logic of science.

The Natural Archives and the Remaking of Time and Climate *Melissa Charenko, Lyman Briggs College, Michigan State University*

In 1892, Albert Seward won the Sedgwick prize for the best essay in geology for his treatise “Fossil Plants as Tests of Climate.” His paper combined botany with geology to “deduce the relative temperatures of various latitudes in the past from such solid data as assemblages of ferns, cycads, and conifers.” Seward’s proposal was one of several recommendations through the late-twentieth-century that suggested that scientists could use remnants of vegetation found in tree rings, sediments at the bottoms of lakes, sloth dung, or packrat middens to understand earth’s history over geologic time. This paper explores the time-making properties of the diverse natural archives used to know past climates. It argues that time and the climate manifested themselves differently depending on which material traces scientists used to study past environments. The yearly temporal resolution of tree rings led to different perceptions of irregular events such as hurricanes compared to the decadal resolution of pollen, which tracked multiyear droughts. Scientists working with these diverse proxies, I suggest, came to different conclusions about the extremes and averages found in the index of past climates. The paper shows how key concepts—climate and time—depend heavily on the ways scientists measure, encounter, and see these concepts through the material reality of vegetation remnants, which in turn had consequences for climate policies.

Session Organizer:

Victor Toom, Netherlands Scientific Council for Government

Policy (WRR)

469. Unpacking biosocial approaches to stress & trauma - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

This panel will bring together scholars researching trauma and stress from biosocial perspectives. Trauma-informed approaches are often positioned as a gold standard of care across biomedical, therapeutic, carceral and policy domains. Historical trauma frameworks have long been central to collective identity and politics among Indigenous, Black and other racially marginalised communities, and have gained momentum through recent anti-racist and anti-colonial movements like Black Lives Matter and Idle No More. Research fields like social epidemiology, critical public health and biological anthropology have explored how trauma and stress “get inside” the body to shape health disparities (e.g. “minority stress”; “weathering” [Geronimus 1992]). Recently, research on the developmental origins of health and disease and epigenetics is redefining trauma as an exposure with a heritable trace (Dubois&Guaspare 2020), raising new questions about ancestral memory and reproductive politics. We invite scholars from various disciplines to explore how trauma and stress are enacted biosocially through human experience, activist tactics, government policy and scientific knowledge. How are trauma and stress defined, studied and reformulated across these arenas? What are the social and political stakes of trauma-informed practices? What forms of temporality, identity and justice do they produce?

Participants:

Turning Extraordinary Adversity Into Research Opportunities:

The New Disciplinary Landscape Of Historical Trauma
Michel Dubois, Gemass - CNRS - Sorbonne; Catherine Guaspare, Gemass-CNRS

The emerging field of social epigenetics has recently redefined historical trauma as a biologically embedded form of adversity (Dubois, Guaspare, 2020). This redefinition transforms the disciplinary landscape usually associated with trauma. Where the latter was a traditional topic for surgery, psychiatry or psychoanalysis (Danieli, 1998), the epigenetic of historical trauma brings in new actors: geneticists, epigeneticists, bioinformaticians, epidemiologists but also anthropologists, sociologists, etc. In a previous study, we highlighted some shifts induced by social epigenetics: from ordinary exposure to extraordinary exposure, from animal models to humans, from individual disorders to the transgenerational dimension of trauma. But who are these scientists transforming the exceptional nature of situations of extreme collective adversity into research opportunities? In this talk, we present some early findings of our ongoing investigation on the dynamics of the field of epigenetics of historical trauma. Based on interviews with the main researchers involved, we develop an original case study for the study of science: how did these researchers get into this specific research area? How do they design and develop their research strategies? Do they perceive the epigenetics of historical traumas as a field of research in its own right? Since researchers are not alone in contributing to the redefinition of the concept of historical trauma, we will be particularly interested in their perceptions and interpretations of the political, cultural and social stakes of their work (Yehuda, Lehmer, Bierer, 2018).

Understanding the biological and psychiatric legacies of intergenerational trauma from South African apartheid: towards an anti-racist science
Andrew Wooyoung Kim, Harvard Medical School

Communities across the globe have witnessed the lingering impacts of unresolved ancestral trauma and historical violence on the health and well-being of subsequent generations. Scientists have recently begun to trace the biological mechanisms that potentially underlie the transmission of intergenerational trauma, and the current psychiatric literature suggests that early life trauma faced during childhood and potentially in utero may become biologically embodied and shape the future child's

lifetime risk for future disease. While the alarming burden of trauma-related mental illnesses in communities with long histories of societal trauma highlights the need for this research, the ongoing legacies of eugenics and scientific racism experienced among such “historically traumatized” communities call into question the political, ethical, and moral stakes involved in this new biological research agenda. I explore these questions through data from an anthropological study on the intergenerational biological effects of trauma and political violence from South African apartheid based in Soweto, South Africa. I examine the deep potential for reifying violent colonial and eugenic logics in South Africa, discuss possible ethnographic and epidemiological opportunities to reject these dynamics in research, and propose new theoretical and methodological engagements to work towards a more politically engaged study of intergenerational trauma.

Public Policy's Uses of Colonial Trauma
Jodie Kidd

This paper is interested in the ways that the concept of historical trauma is used by public policymakers and the effects of these uses. Within the wider context of commitments to evidence-based and culturally-safe policy, Australian policymakers are increasingly taking up the concept of historical or colonial trauma as a way of understanding and addressing ‘gaps’ in social outcomes between Indigenous and non-Indigenous peoples. In this way, historical trauma has become a policy ‘problem’. The paper analyses the problematisation of historical trauma within contemporary child protection policy in three Australian states. It argues that, primarily, historical trauma is understood as a ‘risk factor’ for poor child protection outcomes. This problematisation reflects four central, interconnected concerns. First is a concern over gaps or disparities between Indigenous and non-Indigenous Australians, which frames much Indigenous policy nationally, across several policy areas. Within this larger concern are specific concerns relevant (but not necessarily exclusive) to trauma; a concern over Indigenous child development, over ‘transmission’ of trauma (or damage), and over how to understand/address the persistent social, emotional, and psychological impact of colonisation. The paper discusses some of the antecedents of these policy concerns as well as the implications of primarily understanding and addressing trauma within the framework of risk, within the context of decolonising scholarship.

“We Can’t Wait That Long”: Risk, Refusal and Indigenous Epigenetics
Jaya Keaney, Deakin University; Henrietta Byrne, The University of Adelaide

Environmental epigenetics is increasingly employed to understand the health outcomes of communities who have experienced historical trauma and structural violence. Framing embodiment as inseparable from our social environments, epigenetics provides a way to think about traumatic events as biological “exposures” which lead to poor wellbeing across generations. In Australia, some Indigenous researchers and clinicians are embracing epigenetic science as a framework for theorising the slow violence of colonialism, citing its resonance with Indigenous understandings of personhood (Warin, Kowal & Meloni 2019). However, there is also dispute, contention, and caution among these research communities. This paper traces contention and ambivalence in relation to epigenetics in Indigenous contexts. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork conducted in Australia with researchers and clinicians working in epigenetics and/or Indigenous health, we explore how epigenetics is positioned as risky knowledge with the potential to function as a distraction or an obstacle, particularly at the level of service delivery and primary care. In its supposed novelty and wide public appeal, an emphasis on epigenetics in these contexts risks getting in the way of the deep structural change needed to address the material legacies of colonisation. In the words of one informant, although epigenetics might one day prove useful to front line service delivery, “we can’t wait that long.”

Approaching such sentiments as sites of contest over the politics of epigenetic knowledge, we explore how some participants engage in strategies of refusal (Simpson 2014) when navigating epigenetics and its growing purchase in constructions of Indigeneity, trauma, and healing in Australia.

Biology for Racial Justice? Exploring Biosocial Responses to Trauma and Inequality *Martha Kenney, San Francisco State University; Ruth Müller, MCTS TU München*

Research on the biological effects of early life adversity is increasingly mobilized to affect change in healthcare, education, and juvenile justice (Müller and Kenney 2020). Based on the premise that adverse childhood experiences (ACEs) can change the way bodies respond to stress, actors in these fields have begun to draw on biosocial research to affect change in their institutions to better serve children and youth who have experienced trauma and toxic stress. However, not all institutions readily embrace the biology of early life adversity. In this talk we draw on fieldwork from a large urban school district in California that has encountered these novel biosocial narratives but opted against adopting them as a central part of their programs. Actors at this fieldsite were concerned that these narrative would stigmatize rather than help their students and communities, many of whom were already racialized and pathologized in other ways. Starting from their objections, we consider whether there are research trajectories in the biology of early life adversity capable of supporting the agendas of this school district. In our analysis, we pay particular attention to how biosocial research might detract from or contribute to the district's efforts to achieve racial equity and interrupt the U.S. school-to-prison pipeline and discuss the ambivalence of ACEs and the biology of early life adversity in the context of situated histories and lived experiences of racism. We conclude by asking if and how biologist can study the violence of racism without reifying racial stereotypes and perpetuating oppression.

Session Organizers:

Jaya Keaney, Deakin University
Megan Warin, University of Adelaide
Emma Kowal, Deakin University
Henrietta Byrne, The University of Adelaide

Chair:

Megan Warin, University of Adelaide

470. Critical Computational Relations of Design, Architecture and the Built Environment - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Pop-up Production: Cooperative Tool Development in Architectural Construction *Nadya Peek, University of Washington*

Digital fabrication technology has led to a proliferation of flexible, automated, and distributed manufacturing systems in architectural building. These developments have catalyzed changes from computer-aided design software to manufacturing methods on the shop floor—making coordination of a complex technological network of designers, contractors, sub-contractors, owners, and field erectors the norm for architectural building. In this paper, we highlight the practice of building new, custom tools for coordination and cooperation within the Architecture, Engineering, Construction (AEC) Industry. In particular, we are drawing from participant observation during a three-day workshop conducted with 15 architectural manufacturing professionals including architects, structural engineers, fabricators, and software developers. In the workshop, we compressed the timeline of architectural design, building custom manufacturing machines, and field erection into three days to be able to highlight bottlenecks in the design-to-deployment

workflow and draw attention to shortcomings of current CAD/CAM/manufacturing solutions. We categorize the tools built during the workshop to understand the fabrication workflow practices and artifacts that are formed in conversation with architectural design work. We finally discuss possible future coordination mechanisms which can facilitate highly complex one-off fabrication.

Labor as Concern in Robotics at Carnegie Mellon University, 1980-1989 *Emek Erdolu, Carnegie Mellon University*

This paper reports on the first leg of a doctoral research that investigates the ways robotic technologies reconfigure work in building design and construction. By combining historical and ethnographic research with technical intervention, the doctoral research examines the technical research within history and contemporary robotics to foreground the underlying perspectives on automation and work, and traces the everyday work interactions that robotic technologies condition in contemporary building construction. The first leg historicizes the question of automation and takes Carnegie Mellon University (CMU), a pioneering entity in robotics in the 1980s United States, as a historical site. Through archival documents and oral history interviews, this part of the research captures the motivations, views, and projections of the technology makers of the era on manufacturing and construction automation. It attempts to shed light on the relationship between the discourse on work and robotic systems in the 1980s. As preliminary findings, the paper first presents examples on how labor—at a local and national scale—was an inseparable concern in creating autonomous systems for manufacturing and construction. Secondly, the paper reflects on what is provisionally referred as “human-machine comparison” in this research and the role this outlook in technology design played in inspiring, evaluating, and improving the capabilities of early robotic systems. Lastly, the paper discusses the perspectives on automation and work by the civil engineers, roboticists, architects, and sociotechnical researchers interviewed in relation to the technologies they authored or analyzed.

Technologies of Legibility: Architectural Representation and Surveillant Workflows *Rebecca Smith, Taubman College of Architecture and Urban Planning, University of Michigan*

The inherently racialized and gendered nature of surveillance technologies has been discussed extensively: for their role in replicating structural systems of inequality (Benjamin 2019, Browne 2015), and for the rigidity they impose through the artificial classification and sorting of social identities (Bowker and Star 1999, Cheney-Lippold 2017, Chun 2005). This paper enters into this discussion from an architectural position, by considering the “design” of surveillance systems through various stages of representation. It considers the static, universal, and identical nature of CAD-blocks, in comparison with the larger workflow of surveillance technology, including the automated – but iterative – identification of people, spaces, and objects through machine-learning processes. It asks, what forms of objecthood and subjectivity are allowed or prevented by these workflows? How do they reduce or shut down the potential for multiplicity, ambiguity, and irregularity? This paper places these design processes as unavoidably integrated into larger, socio-material-technical assemblages, in which the “human factor” is never removed: a factor coded as “glitch”, but which actually registers the true functioning of the system (Nakamura 2013). I support this with feminist STS theorizations of the expanded social field of technological solutionism (Suchman 2002, Haraway 1988). I focus on the design of surveillance for public space, because, similarly to public space, surveillance technology is often framed as having a neutral or objective baseline, one rooted in an idea of a universal subject. To counter this, urbanist perspectives emphasizing the role of autonomy and difference (Deutsche 1996, Fraser 1990), will be discussed in relation to the procedures and techniques of architectural representation.

Building an Algorithmic Thought in Computational Design

Yana Boeva, University of Stuttgart

Computational design presents a vast ecology of integrated digital and computational technologies and approaches, as well as a “post-disciplinary pursuit that operates at the intersection of science, engineering, architecture, and design” (Gardner et al. 2020, 7). Integrating algorithmic thought and processes plays a key role in computational design. Computation and algorithmic intelligence generate a shift from designing the form to designing the process with code in mind. However, the requirement of being able to generate code, modify it, and interpretatively explore design options hinders the broader adoption of computational design. The recent development of generative design tools by global CAD software companies and new actors like Sidewalk Labs proposes a solution. These tools also rely on integrating large amounts of design, construction, and urban data and creating new ones. Computational design, however, requires more than technical skills but also an understanding of how technology-related changes (re)produce social, cultural, and regulatory issues. For instance, acquiring computational design skills happens within a few academic programs or outside work time, thus imposing barriers “for those with lesser reserves of economic and social capital” (Gardner 2019, 108). The use of commercial tools further suggests that design choices follow algorithmic parameters and their values, leading to injustice and exclusion (Benjamin 2019). The paper argues that computational design vis-à-vis algorithmic intelligence and commercial development necessitates increasing the awareness of computational logics and their social effects. It draws on empirical data from in-depth interviews with computational designers and a literature review on digital architecture and algorithmic cultures.

Session Organizers:

Yana Boeva, University of Stuttgart

Vernelle A Noel, Georgia Institute of Technology

Chair:

Vernelle A Noel, Georgia Institute of Technology

471. Making Early Career Researchers' Voices Heard for Gender Equality II: Precarity, Mobility, Work-Life Imbalances in Research Career Development

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

Precarious research career opportunities, transnational mobilities, and parenthood constrain Early Career Researchers' professional development and personal experiences. This second session provides insights on the impacts, especially for women researchers.

Participants:

Membership without citizenship? Postdoctoral experiences in Switzerland *Nicky Le Feuvre, Lausanne University; Pierre Bataille, Grenoble Alpes University; Marie Sautier, University of Lausanne/Sciences Po Paris*

Irrespective of national and disciplinary specificities, access to an academic career is increasingly selective. In the competition for a limited number of stable or permanent academic positions, recent PhD graduates who want to pursue an academic career face two main challenges. On the one hand, they have to accept a succession of fixed-term, often part-time and badly paid, precarious positions (i.e. “postdocs”), that have become a prerequisite for potential selection to permanent academic jobs. On the second hand, they are usually required to undertake some form of transnational mobility, which may physically distance them from their existing professional and personal networks. In this contribution, we analyse the effects of the combination of precarious employment and geographical displacement on the citizenship experiences of postdocs working in Switzerland. We adopt the notion of ‘probationary citizenship’, initially developed

by migration scholars, to provide new insights into the contradictory expectations placed on this particular group of early-career academics. On the basis of biographical interviews and ethnographic observations, we examine the citizenship challenges faced by postdocs from across the globe who are working in the Swiss academic context, and analyse their implications for the gendering of academic citizenship. We show that the main problem for female postdocs in the Swiss context is not ‘exclusion’ from the academic community, but rather something akin to ‘membership without citizenship’, and draw on these findings to suggest some ideas for the development of a more sustainable ‘gender equality culture’ in the academic context.

The Disruption of the Patriarchal Bargain in STEM: Getting and Moving on from Probationary Citizenship in a case study Irish university *Pat O'Connor, University of Limerick*

Developing Kandiyoti's (1988, 1998) concept of the patriarchal bargain, the article suggests that the hierarchical relationship between probationary citizens and Principal Investigators (PIs) in Science Technology Engineering and Mathematics (STEM) has been fractured by neoliberalism. It draws on qualitative data from 13 probationary citizens, men and women, on two to five-year contracts in an Irish case study university. It shows that although elements of the patriarchal bargain remain, reflected in being chosen by their PI and in an exploitative work situation, the guarantee of a permanent position had disappeared. Roughly half of them had been there for at least seven years but most wanted to stay on. The situation of women was even more fraught than that of their male counterparts because of the gendered construction of that patriarchal bargain. The article raises questions about its viability as a future model for the creation of knowledge in STEM.

Structural Discrimination of Female Scientists as Mothers in German Speaking Countries as Effect of Home-office and Lockdown in Covid-19 Pandemic *Felizitas Sagebiel, University of Wuppertal*

Home-office as health-political recommendation in Corona pandemic is an eco-political milestone in societal development. CO₂ emission stemming from duty stroke will be reduced and dangerous open-plan-offices could close as not so necessary. Without taking gender in account, only employers' need for control and employees' need for contact seem to be a negative result. Employed female scientists who are mothers experience a new un-compatibility between professional and care work when day care centres and schools close because of lockdown. Female scientists, even though they have to work permanently for research, publications and lectures, feel different from male scientists a prior duty to keep their children busy and help them with homework for school at the same time. Studies show fathers not as much engaged in combining household, looking after children and their professional duties (Allmendinger 2021). Is there a rolling back in traditional masculinities? Increase of mostly male violence in private homes could be a further indicator. Obviously mothers' engagement is necessary for the „system“ (so in German public news), but the outcome is unjust. Employed mothers in home-office with children at home together with their conflicts should be made visible and be worth for public news every day. This is not the case, instead, the old-fashioned patriarchal structures of gendered division of labour become revitalised like „Rabenmütter“ concept, especially in German speaking countries. Studies from 2020 show female scientists' disadvantages in decrease of publications, with the danger of academic career breaks with cumulative disadvantages (Caprile et al. 2012).

Session Organizer:

Chloé Mour, CNRS USR 3608

Chair:

Anne-Sophie Godfroy, République des savoirs (CNRS, École

Normale Supérieure, Collège de France)

Discussant:

Areti Damala, CNRS and ENS - REPUBLIQUE DES SAVOIRS -PROJET ACT

472. Frameworks of responsibility that reshape food systems - II:

Agrifood practices

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

This is the second of two sessions dedicated to advancing knowledge about responsibility for sustainable food systems. Drawing from environmental justice and responsible research and innovation literatures, the papers in this session explore the practice of responsabilising in agri-food systems.

Participants:

Agroecology and food communities in Italy: exploring Genuino Clandestino label *Andrea Ghelfi*, *University of Nottingham*

The Genuino Clandestino (Genuine Clandestine in English, GC from now) farmers network was born in 2010 in order to defend the existence of a multiplicity of rural forms of living and promoting agroecology and food sovereignty. GC's practices include, amongst others, grassroots farmers markets, the experimentation of Participatory Guarantee Systems, civic use and collective care of land as commons. The national network emerged through the organisation of a civil disobedience campaign: the label GC, attached to the products on sale in farmers markets, reclaimed the legitimacy of circulating clandestine and genuine agricultural products. Challenging social, legal and health standards governing food production and circulation (especially in relation to processed food such as cheese, marmalade, wine, tomato sauce) these farmers showed how these standards were forged in relation to the infrastructures of industrial food production. The GC label brings with itself not only a series of social and legal controversies implied in small scale food circulation; this anti-logo refers also to the invention of alternative material infrastructures and participatory standards of socio-material sustainability capable of rearticulating the food web from farm to city. Starting from the example of the Campi Aperti Association for Food Sovereignty based in Bologna, in my presentation I will analyse the main features of emergent food communities in which the construction of autonomous standards is synonymous with the experimentation of novel practices of responsibility amongst producers and consumers.

(Re)Making Community Needs within Urban Agricultural Lands on the Edge of Tokyo *Jack Lichten*, *University of Tokyo*

This article examines how Japanese legal designations designed to protect existing agricultural production in urban areas, leave large gaps in economic sustainability for the producer to be filled in by neighbors. Since the 1990s bubble collapse, peri-urban regions in Japan have experienced an increase in population largely through decentralized subdivisions, consuming existing farmland, surrounding forests, and the associated agro-forestry ecosystem. To protect existing farmland in urbanizing areas, the national government established a "Productive Green Zone" designation starting from 1992, which aimed to protect agricultural land through massive property tax breaks. Despite these incentives, this land has seen a steady decline, losing out to more financially-lucrative land uses. In this article, I follow a selection of organizations in a Tokyo fringe suburb aiming to counteract the loss of agricultural land. These community groups maintain the land's agro-forestry ecosystem through a rubric locally known as "satoyama", whose idealized conception required a whole community's cooperation but also provided numerous food, timber, and other resources while also supporting a variety of multi species encounters, though is now perceived as incompatible with modern suburban living. Instead of focusing purely on commodity outputs, the suburban community groups cultivate and emphasize the agro-forestry ecosystem and claim a

multi-generational "satoyama" cultural lineage through the land they maintain - with the farmer's consent, if not cooperation. Using "satoyama" as cultural legitimacy, the groups attempt to incorporate patches of neighboring agricultural land - this work undermines the legal purpose of urban commodity production while opening the land for possibilities related to agricultural & forestry encounters.

The Lands On Which We Grew: Three Acts Of Regrowing Land and Peoples *Leo Matteo Bachinger*, *Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute - STS*

Family farms in upstate New York; farms and vintners in the onsets of the Austrian alps; and a Sacred Forest in a small city in New York's Capital District. In these three places, new relations are grown between land, people and surrounding communities. In of them, three related stories converge: Stories of devastation, marginalization and fracture; of resistance; and of re-building communities through (re-)building community through ecological refiguring. The Sacred Forest in Troy, NY faces an uncertain future, threatened by development. It is a story of rebuilding multiple fractured and marginalized community and indigenous heritage through resistance and food forestry. In upstate New York, regenerative farmers and CSAs strive to rebuild their communities and ecologies, as they are fractured and devastated by industrial and globalized agricultural systems. In Austria, relations with agricultural land as *cultural land* shape how food is grown in, with, through and for the communities — and how farmers resist the pressures of the global food system. This presentation draws on comparative research in agricultural communities in upstate New York and Austria as well as on the ground advocacy work alongside indigenous peoples and local communities in an urban Environmental Justice Area to bring to the forefront critical lessons for how new responsibilities emerge out of at times unexpected places and moments of disruption, resistance, marginalization, fragmentation — and reinvention.

Session Organizer:

Allison Marie Loconto, INRAE

473. Biometrics on the Move - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Biometric practices have moved around the world through colonial and postcolonial contexts, transnational exchange, and private sector developments. They have become central to a variety of public and private infrastructures. Often, biometric technologies and data are not built from scratch, rather they are reformulated and repurposed to fit new times, places, and contexts. Automated face and fingerprint identification on smartphones, and biometric data in ID cards, are underwritten by similar methods of body measurement developed by 19th and 20th century eugenics, anthropology, statistics, and criminology researchers. States have appropriated biometric databases as digital platforms, which often serve as foundations upon which other infrastructures are organized. Biometric systems have been used, and reused, for purposes ranging from the delivery of government services to policing, from tracking refugees to COVID-19 mitigation efforts. This open track invites submissions that address the movement of biometric practices, and their social consequences. Panelists will explore not only how biometric techniques constitute emerging forms of identity governance, but also how they move across time and place, reorganize existing practices, and produce new kinds of infrastructures. Even in new contexts, biometric systems carry the biases and intentions of prior ones. These systems can fail, and present asymmetrical benefits and harms that reinforce inequalities related to race, gender, class, age, and disability. These systems also shape the lived experiences of citizenship, migration, surveillance, and access to services. This panel welcomes papers that leverage STS concepts and methods to probe the trajectories, implementations, and implications of biometrics on the move.

Participants:

Postcolonial Apocalypse: Biometrics, IDs, and Governance in

Jamaica Kimberley McKinson, *John Jay College, CUNY*

In 2017, the Jamaican government communicated its intention to introduce a National Identification System (NIDS), which would house biographic, biometric, and demographic information. After the announcement, deep suspicions arose about the government's desire to provide each citizen with a unique identification number and secure biometric data. For some, NIDS was read as an apocalyptic reference to the Mark of the Beast, as detailed in the Book of Revelations. For others, the move to collect biometric data was taken to be an act of warfare against the liberty of the Jamaican people. In this paper, I draw on my ethnographic research in Kingston in order to interrogate NIDS as an infrastructure of postcolonial datafication governance (Arora 2016), one that embodies simultaneously biblical, spatial, and corporeal fears of insecurity in a Caribbean geography that lies in the shadow of the plantation. What is at stake in a post-colonial landscape, with the merging of the body and a technology predicated on state legitimized techniques of branding and control? In paying attention to discourses of racialization and emancipation surrounding NIDS, I argue for a reading of the Caribbean that positions it as a critical geographical lens through which to consider Simone Browne's (2015) contention that blackness is a key site through which surveillance is both practiced and creatively resisted. In responding to the call for the decolonization of STS, this reflection takes seriously what the Caribbean can contribute to our understandings of the possibilities of black emancipation in the present moment of global surveillance.

Children and digital identities in Kenya- efficiency or overreach? *Grace Mutung'u, Centre for IP and IT Law, Strathmore University; Isaac Rutenberg, Centre for IP and IT Law, Strathmore University*

While Kenya has had a national legal identification system since before independence, issuance of identities to children is a novel practice. It was first implemented in 2016 under the National Education Management Information System (NEMIS) where school children were issued with unique personal identifiers that were linked to their birth certificates and parents' identity documents. Collection of children's biometrics is set to start under a new national system known as Huduma Namba. This is with the reasoning that digital identity will enable children to better access government services, enhance their right parental care and protection and also aid in faster resolution of cases of child trafficking. Digital identities are issued under a system which envisages centralised management of personal identity under the Ministry of Interior and Coordination of National Government. In a judgement following a petition contesting Huduma Namba, issues raised with regard to children's digital identity data included: special protection needed to protect children from surveillance overreach; consideration of the evolving nature of children; and mechanisms for transition of children into age of majority. Our research explores how children's digital identities affect their social, cultural and national citizenship. It analyses policies, laws and practices on children's identity to reflect on the relationship that digital identities create between the children and government and its effect for the children who do not obtain the identities. The research uses a social justice lens to analyse the sufficiency and sustainability of Kenya's digital identity technologies in protecting and promoting children's citizenship.

Moves toward Universal Health Coverage and the biometric state in Kenya *Ruth Prince, University of Oslo*

Since 2018, Kenya's moves towards Universal Health Coverage – a programme that seeks to ensure “everyone has access to the healthcare they need without financial hardship” – has involved intense forms of registration of citizens for experiments with free healthcare. At the same time the Kenyan government has been rolling out a nation-wide biometric registration drive, Huduma

Namba, aiming to create a national biometric identification system. Attending to how these processes unfolded on the ground, in this paper I explore how these parallel projects to count citizens and create welfare and healthcare beneficiaries make people visible to the state and the private sector in particular ways. These experiments with digital and biometric registration also offer insights into emerging relations between the state, private enterprise, digital technology, NGOs, healthcare, and data in an east African state.

Biometric Social Protection: An Historical Evolution Narrative *Silvia Masiero, University of Oslo*

Biometric Social Protection (BSP), defined as the turn of social protection schemes to biometric identification and authentication of recipients, has evolved significantly over time. While spatial variation is largely accounted for, with multiple accounts of BSP across regions and countries, less attention is devoted to the evolution of BSP over time, from its early days to the adaptations made in response to the COVID-19 pandemic. Against this backdrop, this paper relies on core concepts from the Social Shaping of Technology (MacKenzie & Wajcman, 1999) to propose a historical narrative of the evolution of biometric social protection schemes over time. Framing biometrics as a sociotechnical construct, I combine literature and field resources to delineate a three-phase evolution of BSP: a first phase (late 1990s-ca.2010), named a development turn of biometrics, pictured BSP largely as a route to combat the exclusion of entitled recipients from programmes. A second phase (ca.2010-2020), building on the development turn, moved the focus to targeted social protection, leading programme designers to tackle inclusion errors through BSP. Finally, the COVID-19 pandemic (2020-present) inaugurated a novel, sudden phase of reconception, in which BSP needs fast adaptations to deal with large numbers of new poor. My analysis combines SST with the illumination of data-based forms of injustice, or data injustices, emerging through the three phases. In doing so, the paper contributes to STS and data justice literatures, making a case for valuing their intersection. References: MacKenzie, D., & Wajcman, J. (1999). *The social shaping of technology*. London: Open University Press.

Session Organizer:

Michelle Spektor, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Chair:

Ranjit Pal Singh, Data & Society Research Institute

474. Democracy, (In)Security, and Technology - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

Participants:

Questioning The AI Origins of Dictatorship and Democracy
Scott Timcke

Set against a near two decades 'global democratic recession', of late a line of analysis has emerged within the US foreign policy community that suggests that 'authoritarian states' like China and Russia are poised to best reap the economic windfall that technologies like artificial intelligence and machine learning will bring in the decades ahead. Supposedly, these technologies allow authoritarians to skirt the growth trap that their political economies typically feature, meaning that these states can use their coercion power to control the mass unemployment of workers displaced by automation thereby avoiding political disruptions that could compromise economic performance in democratic states. The same kinds of technologies that made surplus populations will be used by authoritarians to further consolidate their power giving rise to 'digital dictatorships' that erode human agency, subvert human desires, and generally make liberal democracy with their free-market economics obsolete. Aside from revisiting assumptions about the durability of nominally democratic societies, these analysts are ideating

whether, should the US state desire to preserve global hegemony, it too should follow the same course as the authoritarians and accept how these technologies slant away from democratic affordance. Drawing upon the critical theory of technology, this presentation offers a forthright rebuttal of these views, showing how they rest on faulty assumptions about how technology is adopted in institutions, the relationship of technology to economic outcomes, and the source of economic growth.

Science Otherwise: Migrant innovation and hybrid technologies in/of the Mexican Borderlands. *Lindsay Adams Smith, Arizona State University*

In the face of a migration crisis, with an estimated 70,000-120,000 migrants disappeared in the Mexican borderlands in the last ten years, and a militarized and ever-shifting enforcement regime at both Mexico's northern and southern border, migrants and activists are relying on emerging digital and forensic technologies to navigate these indeterminate spaces. In this paper, I draw on the work of Arturo Escobar and his colleagues in the coloniality/modernity group to think through the place of innovation, science, and forensic practice by migrants and activists. I offer the concept of "Science Otherwise" as a critique of the language of "citizen science" to ask how we can attend to the politics, world-building and imaginaries on the move. Drawing on 28 months of ethnographic fieldwork with activists, migrants, and scientists in the Mexican borderlands, I show how migrants innovate with technology to better address their concerns, be it communication, navigation, help when in danger, family reunification, or justice. This paper focuses on the ways in which migrants and advocates innovate with and transform technology to serve their ends, within a larger overdetermined sociotechnical landscape by mapping four emergent border technologies: biometrics, ICT & GPS technology, forensic DNA, and isotope analysis. Taken together these technologies highlight (1) borders as spaces of innovation and experimentation on the part of migrants and (2) the role of the border laboratory in making visible the borderlands vibrant hybridities.

Social Networks and Visual Evidence of Police Violence in Colombia. Police Abuse and Alternative Forms of Evidence in the Making. *Derly Sanchez, Derly Sánchez; Oscar Maldonado, Universidad del Rosario; Javier Guerrero-C, Instituto Tecnológico Metropolitano; DISORLAB Team, Universidad del Rosario*

On November 21st of 2020, the Colombian police's anti-riot squad killed a protester (Dillan Cruz). Less than one year later, on September 9th of 2021, police agents apprehended and killed a citizen (Javier Ordoñez). This later killing was followed by protests against police brutality, which ended in killing at least another 13 persons by the police. Inspired by the concerns of digital sociology (Marres, 2017) and STS for the digital (Venturini and others, 2019) and digital infrastructure, our interest is to capture digital interactions and analyze the emergence of matters of concern (Marres, 2017) around police violence. We present the mechanisms of dissemination of police violence reports by citizens on social networks. We analyzed data collected using Netlytic, MAXQDA, and Gephi from social networks such as Twitter and Facebook, with a strategy that contemplated various involvement with the data (Nonnecke and others, 2019; Gruzd and Mai, 2020). Quantitative analysis of networks metrics and discursive analysis and the ethnographic moments that emerged from participant observation with the data (Hine, 2015) and device-data-observation intra-actions (Barad, 2007). This exploration wants to understand the emergence of citizen strategies to construct new forms of evidence as resistance and defiance to the media and the State's official narratives, resonating with the invitation of data feminism (D'Ignazio and Klein, 2020) to identify and challenge power. We understand the circulation of videos as denunciation, a challenge to authority in which citizens use tools to monitor those who have the role of

policing (Mann, et al. 2003).

The Good Spy vs. the Bad Spy: Legitimizing Surveillance, Challenging Democracy *Dan M. Kotliar, Department of Communication, Stanford University; Elinor Carmi, Liverpool University, UK.*

This paper focuses on the way surveillance is negotiated and legitimized in democratic societies while challenging their legal and territorial boundaries. We explore this through a critical analysis of the WhatsApp v. NSO Group legal feud, which revolves around NSO's alleged attempts to hack into human rights activists' phones through WhatsApp's infrastructure. Based on discourse analysis of legal documents, journalistic reports and interviews, corporate papers, and a historical analysis of NSO's website, we argue that companies' legitimation strategies differ according to their social, political, and international position. We highlight the specific ways in which these two companies use this legal feud to legitimize their surveillance, reaffirm their data jurisdiction, and normalize their business practices. Specifically, we expose the discourses, narratives, and ideologies through which this legitimation takes place, and the ways such data-intensive companies assert their rights over people's data. Our findings also shed light on these companies' relationships with other powers and institutions (e.g. the state, the courts, the military, or the international community) in constructing and maintaining their surveillance empires. While previous research highlighted the legitimation of surveillance by the press or the market, this research shows how such companies actively legitimize their intrusive technologies in their own voice. Finally, we show that the normalization of surveillance requires ongoing persuasion, justification, and negotiation, especially in times of global privacy awareness.

Session Organizer:

Scott Timcke

475. Innovation, STS and Good Relations: Building Sociotechnical Futures in Unequal and Uncertain Worlds - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Innovation is a central element within public and private discussions over the form and direction of socio-technical change. However, 'innovation' as a topic presents STS scholars with a number of closely-related dilemmas. Is our role to deconstruct and challenge the very idea of innovation or else to seek ways of augmenting and developing it in a more socially-engaged and responsible fashion? Should we view innovation as a source of social and environmental challenges or else as a positive means of addressing those same challenges? Given the fast-expanding literature within Innovation Studies in particular, should STS scholars seek to build intellectual bridges with neighbouring disciplines or else develop more distinctive theoretical and empirical perspectives? Faced with uncertain and unequal worlds, is innovation – and innovation scholarship – part of the problem or the solution? In this session, we invite contributions from STS scholars whose work addresses the interface between innovation, STS and 'good relations': including global issues of inequality and uncertainty. We welcome empirical studies exploring innovation in specific contexts but also those which seek new conceptual possibilities regarding STS and innovation. What is – and what should be – the relationship between STS scholarship, innovation and the building of stronger social and environmental relations? And what does this mean for the future governance and practice of innovation? Potential topics include: Innovation, futures, governance, challenges, uncertainty

Participants:

Future-making and Transformative Promises : Visionary or Illusory? *Nishtha Bharti, Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi*

The Science, Technology, and Innovation Policy 2020 (STIP 2020) - the fifth national science, technology and innovation policy of India since its Independence in 1947, was released amidst the cataclysm of the Covid-19 pandemic. Its most recent

draft is the embodiment of a grandiose vision, projecting techno-scientific futures that are deemed at once desirable and inevitable. The document is an exercise in grandstanding - offering to transform the national STI landscape by setting up numerous funds, institutions and frameworks in almost every chapter, ostensibly to remove all roadblocks in the path of acquiring equity and inclusivity. At the same time, the STIP 2020 decidedly steers away from a reflexive assessment of past efforts in the realm of innovation policy-making, from identifying gaps in the present system, and from any proposal of dialogue and collaboration with related ministries and departments (Abrol, 2021). Through my paper, I would argue that this tendency of generic superfluity around scientific and technological innovations is a recurring feature in the policy pronouncements of the Government of India, and indicates a practise of future-making that not only shapes the direction and governance of innovation but more importantly, the identification of problems that actually need concerted intervention of public and private actors. The analytical purchase afforded by probing future-making practices concerning science and technology ventures is often underscored in STS scholarship, such as through the tropes of imaginaries (Jasanoff & Kim, 2009, 2015) or expectations (Van Lente & Rip, 1998; Brown, 2003; Borup et al., 2006). Drawing on a discursive analysis of select policy documents and mobilizing concepts from the aforementioned literature, I would examine the contours of future-making on behalf of the Indian state, and the implications of its integration into policy and innovation processes. In particular, I would strive to highlight that such a move conceals the deliberate policy silences around the pressing needs of an unequal socio-political order and at the same time, occludes any accountability from addressing those needs/issues.

Science and innovation (S&I) policy in China and the United States: national policy mixes for a knowledge-based economy Xuan Li; Aixa Aleman-Diaz, *Copenhagen Business School*

In the last decades, countries have converged towards building knowledge-based economies under the assumption that leveraging technology and innovation will unleash beneficial economic forces. China and the US have become global leaders in this trend. However, the effort to build knowledge-based economies takes distinctive national forms in which particular 'policy mixes'—different combination of policy instruments – support the process of building socio-technical futures. In the context of an increasingly ferocious US-China tech competition, we seek to compare the policy instruments that these countries have deployed over the last twenty years to realize a knowledge-based economy. This paper looks into 10 national science and innovation policy documents from China and US, dating between 2004 and 2020, to explore how national 'policy mixes' reflect the changing mechanisms of the state-market relationship. In turn, these mechanisms have helped shape the form of research and innovation policy-making in the two countries. The paper thus sheds light on the changing narratives of science and innovation policy in two countries. The pathways pursued by China and the US can provide insights into both contextual distinctiveness and patterns of convergence and familiarity. We contribute to the theoretical understanding of these ideas in the STS literature by applying the term "isomorphic difference" to capture the spread and translation of ideas within and across contexts.

Societal Implications of System Innovations: A New Configurational Framework for Studying the Socio-technical Implications of Energy Transitions Michael Ornetzeder, *Austrian Academy of Sciences*; Titus Udrea, *Austrian Academy of Sciences, Inst. of Technology Assessment (ITA)*; Tanja Sinoszic, *Austrian Academy of Sciences*

The energy transition will involve new technologies and infrastructures, as well as new institutions and practices.

However, the strong emphasis on decarbonization runs the risk of 'technocratic reduction' leading to new technological fixes and undesirable side effects. STS research has the conceptual potential, however, to ensure that the various implications of innovations are examined in broad, systemic configurational contexts. This paper proposes a new approach for systematically assessing the societal implications of emerging innovations in the context of transition processes. Conceptually bridging transition research, technology assessment, and complex systems approaches, we explore how consequences emerge from different socio-technical configurations and how we can better understand the implications of such configurations. In this paper, we empirically apply our framework using the case of decentralised electricity generation. This illustrative case shows how even similar configurations of household photovoltaic and stationary battery systems may lead to rather different societal implications. Specifically, we show how distinct configurations relate to generated electricity and the share of energy autonomy of households, implying different local, regional, and systemic effects. With socio-technical configurations in the center of the analysis, we deepen and simultaneously broaden our understanding of ongoing variation in the energy system. We argue that such a configurational perspective is essential if we are to ensure that future developments do not lead to new technological fixes and negative path dependencies, but remain open to change and adaptation.

Innovation, AI English-Education, and Neoliberal Relations In Kim, *Seoul National University, Republic of Korea*

To deconstruct the idea of innovation, I analyze how meaning of innovation among actors is translated differently in forming the network of education, in a case study. Three entities co-produce assemblage network in education, combined with non-human actants of technology. For public sector(government), innovation is translated as a change of socio-technical regime. For private sector(industry), it is translated as a competence in the market. For individuals, innovation is translated as a self-development, not only concerning technology but also concerning one's life as an entrepreneur, faced with inequality and uncertainty of neoliberalism. In this network, individuals are re-configured from technology-user, to capital resource of technology. Neoliberalism penetrates this assemblage of innovation, by ideals such as competition, free market and improvement. In this sense, human capital is not only the core concept of neoliberalism, but also of educational technology. As a case-study, I focus on 'AI innovation wave' of English-education in Korea, analyzing interactions of three entities mentioned above(government, industry, individuals). In Korea, English education, echoing neoliberal political-economy of globalization, reinforces individual inequality in global competition. Resorting to AI and its informational nudge, individuals' behaviors are immersed in neoliberal governmentality. By analyzing AI algorithm & data, I explain how AI education in closed system masks the uncertainty and inequality of the world. Drawn from the case of Korea, Good relations in education, I argue, is neither about meritocracy nor technocracy, but about equal chances(as opposed to meritocratic opportunity) and diversity.

Neuralink Insights for Data Governance and the Role of Sociotechnical Imaginaries in the Smart City Elma Hajric, *SFIS - Arizona State University*

With Elon Musk's techno-utopian imaginary taking shape in the form of a brain implant device known as Neuralink, and goals to commercialize this, there are risks and ethical considerations that must be taken into account. This paper discusses these considerations of this futuristic technology, and situates them with emerging data governance concepts and smart city imaginaries of the future, arguing for the need to build in more anticipatory governance and awareness of emerging technologies into the current approaches. The paper's methodology reviews existing Deep Brain Simulation (DBS) literature for identifying

ethical considerations, and weaves in STS literature regarding sociotechnical imaginaries and anticipatory governance, along with reviewing mixed-media availability on developing commercial implants and brainwave-reading devices, such as Neuralink. The analysis involves scenarios to identify ethical concerns and risks within a smart city context being shaped by the sociotechnical imaginaries of Elon Musk.

Ecosystem Scenarios As Participatory Science Communication

Shift Socioecological Innovation Towards Integrative Research And Management *Ludwig Weh, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin; Charlotte Weil, École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne*

Participatory science communication has supported multi-level, multi-actor decision-making with ecosystem scenarios (Carpenter et al. 2006, Alcamo 2008, Moss et al. 2010, van Vuuren et al. 2012), driving integrated socioecological innovation in sustainable decision and management strategies on individual, organizational, societal levels. This paper discusses conceptual and theoretical premises of decision support tools co-producing scenario-based orientation knowledge and confining environmental uncertainty to manageable dimensions. To serve mutually beneficial human-nature relationships, innovative ecological practices must be socially integrated, accepted and promoted across sectors and scales. For that, Luhmann's (2018) concept of uncertainty absorption demands uncertainty not be reduced below a vital level without which an organization "would cease to exist for lack of activity" (ibid., p. 149). In socioecological discourse, STS scholars consulting to organizational decision-making thus face challenges to balance uncertainty reduction with sufficient uncertainty reproduction, avoiding deterministic predictions and presenting alternatives for future legitimization of organizations' activity. Especially circular approaches tackling planetary overuse are critical of unregulated, linear economic growth and demand relational review and reframing of ecological innovation towards mindful, dependable and caring solutions (Chan et al. 2012, Jax et al. 2018). In this, social capital production for natural capital preservation makes ecosystem scenarios an insightful case to study actor relations as novel quality criterion of scenario research (MA 2003, Lang et al. 2017). Future innovation scholarship in the field should create structural, intellectual and relational benefits through activating, discursive, participatory approaches, shifting profit-driven innovation towards sustainable, responsible and socially integrated practices, as reflected in Integrated Assessment research. Alcamo, J. (Ed.). (2008). *Environmental futures: the practice of environmental scenario analysis*. Elsevier. Carpenter, S. R., Bennett, E. M., & Peterson, G. D. (2006). Scenarios for ecosystem services: an overview. *Ecology and Society*, 11(1). Chan, K. M., Guerry, A. D., Balvanera, P., Klain, S., Satterfield, T., Basurto, X., ... & Woodside, U. (2012). Where are cultural and social in ecosystem services? A framework for constructive engagement. *BioScience*, 62(8), 744-756. Jax, K., Calestani, M., Chan, K. M., Eser, U., Keune, H., Muraca, B., ... & Wittmer, H. (2018). Caring for nature matters: a relational approach for understanding nature's contributions to human well-being. *Current opinion in environmental sustainability*, 35, 22-29. Lang, T., & Ramirez, R. (2017). Building new social capital with scenario planning. *Technological forecasting and social change*, 124, 51-65. Luhmann, N. (2018). *Organization and Decision* (D. Baecker, Ed.; R. Barrett, Trans.). Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. MA (2003). *Ecosystems and human well-being: a framework for assessment*. Millennium Ecosystem Assessment. Washington, DC: Island press. Moss, R. H., Edmonds, J. A., Hibbard, K. A., Manning, M. R., Rose, S. K., Van Vuuren, D. P., Meehl, G. A. (2010). The next generation of scenarios for climate change research and assessment. *Nature*, 463(7282), 747-756. Van Vuuren, D. P., Kok, M. T., Girod, B., Lucas, P. L., & de Vries, B. (2012). Scenarios in global environmental assessments: key

characteristics and lessons for future use. *Global Environmental Change*, 22(4), 884-895.

Session Organizers:

Alan Irwin, Copenhagen Business School

Jane Bjørn Vedel, Copenhagen Business School

Chair:

Jane Bjørn Vedel, Copenhagen Business School

476. Innovative biotechnologies, co-regulation and bionetworking II: Challenging/contested Innovations

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Repeatedly, when medical scientists propose the authorization of new biotechnologies, fears and hopes emerge alongside new impasses, legal frictions, and uncertainties. This applies, for example, to cutting-edge therapies potentially capable of treating chronic diseases and, hence, of substituting pharmaceuticals that are currently in use (sometimes paradigmatically). While navigating between this skepticism towards regulatory authorities and reassurances of faith in science, which biopolitical agendas are enacted and disseminated by the proposed biotechnologies in contemporary health innovation arenas? This panel aims to explore the impacts of new health technologies on different societies and how, in turn, multiple actors affect them, including their evaluation processes, design and related policies. The panel invites contributions that address aspects of the development, circulation, and co-regulation of novel biotechnologies as relatable to forms of bionetworking (e.g. judicialization, biohacking, infrastructuring, co-production of expertise and digital activism). Bionetworking practices comprise collaborative relationships between scientists, patients, their caretakers, and other actors (including biological, legal, and entrepreneurial ones), to support and/or disqualify promising biotechnologies. In light of this, the panel provides a platform to discuss the actuality of concepts linked to the STS-field of biocitizenship like political economies of hope, life assemblages, adoption space, among others. It looks to discuss controversies in areas such as vaccinology, regenerative medicine, gene therapy, translational and precision medicine, microbiome-based therapies, and experimental therapies more broadly. A central point of reflection concerns how tensions between different ways of assessing the efficacy and innovativeness of proposed biotechnologies, and of co-producing medical evidence, might become co-constitutive of biosocialities.

Participants:

Resolving Dualisms: Trainer Approaches To Reconcile Cybersecurity With Healthcare Practices *Tessa Oomen, Erasmus Universiteit Rotterdam; Jason Pridmore, Erasmus University*

The healthcare industry has undergone a "digital revolution", however, without sufficient security considerations. Healthcare is thus a highly vulnerable sector, carrying potential risks to human life, quality of care, and the security of highly sensitive data. Strategies to improve cybersecurity often take an either/or perspective, perpetuating the dualistic notion of technology versus social. We argue that reframing cybersecurity as a practice allows social actors such as trainers, healthcare practitioners, and managers (amongst others), a new approach to improving professional healthcare practices. We foreground the interplay between sociomaterial, knowledge, and emotional elements of practices to provide a rich understanding of cybersecurity. Through semi-structured qualitative interviews with cybersecurity trainers across the European Union (e.g., data privacy officers, security officers, information security consultants), we studied how trainers support healthcare employees to make sense of technology in their daily work. We found that trainers are key organizational members for bridging existing dualisms in healthcare contexts. They aim to resolve the relationship between healthcare worker and medical technologies, as well as between patient care and cybersecurity. Trainers start from the idea that healthcare workers shape the use of technology as much as the technology shapes their daily work,

and that this requires not just particular knowledge or skills to handle materials, but also involves emotional and motivational components that current cybersecurity training/education interventions do not incorporate. This study offers a new sociomaterial approach to study cybersecurity, both in healthcare and beyond, as well as a new way to address cybersecurity in practical contexts.

Let X Be Unknown: the Epistemology of Digital Psychedelic Inquiry *Emma Stamm, Villanova University*

Contemporary research on psychedelic-assisted psychiatry must reckon with digital epistemologies. Digital methods challenge psychedelic researchers insofar as data appear to inadequately represent the qualitative character of psychedelic experience. By most accounts, the effects of psychedelic ingestion are particular to each individual and atypical of ordinary experience. Multiple scholars have noted that the epistemic virtues promoted by digital methodology — including objectivity, capacity for positive representation and standardizability — contrast with the palliative properties of psychedelics, which are notably non-positive. The difficulties of translating the subjective dimension of psychedelic treatment into data have led some to critique the rote use of digital methods in this field. If digital methodologies presuppose ontic or epistemic commensurability between various realms of experience, they argue, they might foreclose the articulation of the therapeutically effective qualities of psychedelics. My paper reads psychedelic psychiatry publications alongside articles from philosophers of science to indicate the following: many psychedelic researchers resolve this paradox by envisioning persons not as figures, but as iterative patterns available to partial digital representation. These patterns are denied the psychological investment conventionally accorded to “persons.” The metaphor of “depth” to describe the object allegedly recalcitrant to data-intensive hermeneutics is forsaken in favor of the “flat” person-as-pattern immanent with shifting experience. These researchers, however, are not behaviorist. They consider that if “deep” facets of personhood are real, such facets exist beyond any operable conception of the “person.” That which psychedelic research discounts from data is therefore figured out of all forms of positive intelligibility.

Replacing mosquitoes: the use of biotechnology to control arboviruses *Claudia Santos Turco, HCTE-UFRJ / FIOCRUZ; EDUARDO N PAIVA, EDUARDO NAZARETH PAIVA*

The relationship between humans and *Aedes aegypti* has a long history. This mosquito was identified as an “enemy” more than 100 years ago, with the establishment of the yellow fever transmission cycle. The importance given to its population control in Brazil has grown again since the 1980s, with the recurrent dengue epidemics and, later, the arrival of Zika and Chikungunya viruses. The arrival of the Zika virus in Brazil, in 2015, rekindled old controversies and created new ones involving the control of arboviruses. Controversies related to the control of the *Aedes aegypti* population have returned with intensity. The difficulties faced in relation to the control of epidemics whose vector is *Aedes aegypti* became evident. In this context, a new technology - already in development in Brazil since 2012 - started a process of scaling up: the *Aedes aegypti* mosquitoes infected with the bacteria *Wolbachia*. This technology is part of a new paradigm in vector control that changes spraying with insecticides for the rear and release of mosquitoes created in the laboratory. It is also a technology that does not aim at suppressing or controlling mosquito populations, but at replacing it by a new one. The present work seeks to map the sociotechnical networks formed during the exit of the *Aedes aegypti* with *Wolbachia* from the laboratory benches to different neighborhoods in two Brazilian cities, from 2012 to 2015. The associations established, the relationship with other technologies and their regulatory process still pending will be addressed.

Biotechnological Innovation, Internet and Biosociality: A Case Study on the Co-Production of Medical Evidence in Brazil *Márcio Vilar, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany*

In 2008, an online forum was initiated in Brazil to deliberate on the efficacy of a drug to treat autoimmunity whose manufacturing, commercialization and distribution had been forbidden in 2005. The drug in question, ‘the vaccine’, was originally developed by medical scientists and had been in use since the 1980s. Yet, it remained predominantly ignored in public health debates. Until 2017, forum participants, posted messages to either promote or disqualify the vaccine’s use, reporting personal experiences with it, detailing its effects and sharing contacts of related professionals and internet links, including a petition for its regularization. This forum was just one among other virtual platforms that people used interchangeably, and which have superseded handwritten letters. Given that, which biopolitical agenda does ‘the vaccine’ disseminate and enact in the internet? In this proposal, I explore how biotechnological innovation, internet and biosociality intertwine and co-evolve within a Global South setting. Informed by participant observation and further fieldwork activities, I consider the discussions on the vaccine’s efficacy and use as bionetworking practices. These may imply modalities of intervention that made it possible for participants to discuss medical dogmas and taboos publicly, and eventually embarking on medico-legal transgression. Besides, many not only evaluated the vaccine as an immunostimulant promise but also questioned the rationale of conventional treatments based on immunosuppression. My hypothesis is that by enacting a biopolitics from below through digitally framed exchanges of therapeutic experiences, forum participants managed, despite prohibition, to recreate adoption spaces for the vaccine as a potential medical future.

Session Organizer:

Márcio Vilar, Goethe University Frankfurt, Germany

Discussant:

Carlos Novas, Carleton University

477. The Biomedicalization of Social Medicine? - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Biomedicalization scholars have argued that studies of biomedicalization need to be situated in their geopolitical context and within that context’s history of approaches to health and healing (Clarke et al 2010). Biomedicalization can be absent in some sites, or it can be contested by a diverse set of other approaches to healing (such as non-Western practices of medicine). Yet such contestations within the field of medicine itself have often been overlooked in the literature on biomedicalization. One such field is social medicine, a field concerned with the social determinants of health and the relations of medicine and social justice. In this panel, we trace the blurred and contested boundaries between social medicine and biomedicine. Some practices of social medicine have included at the same time social forms of care and biomedicalized approaches. Other social medicine practices have explicitly challenged biomedicalization processes. At different times and places, proponents of social medicine have argued that it has been too much biomedicine (at the expense of social, political and legal approaches), or that it has been too little of it (HIV treatment in low income countries, access to gender-affirming therapy). Sometimes, biomedicalization processes initially promoted by social medicine in the name of solidarity or health equity, have been transformed into more techno-science-dependent forms of practice, sometimes in stratified forms. In this open panel, we aim to explore diverse empirical examples of interdependencies, interconnectedness and contestations between biomedicine and social medicine in different historical and contemporary sites.

Participants:

A clinical understanding of biomedicine and social medicine, the French tuberculosis chemoprophylaxis controversy
Kylian Godde, EHESP, Cermes3

In France, at the end of the fifties, social medicine practitioners experiment the use of an antibiotic (INH) in chemoprophylaxis on children for tuberculosis prevention. It's the beginning of a controversy about the best preventive method between the INH, mostly supported by pediatrician, and the BCG vaccination defended by tuberculosis specialists. The refusal of INH by the latter has nothing to do with the introduction of a biomedicine artefact in social medicine or the technical possibility of such chemoprophylaxis: tuberculosis specialists have gotten to grips with laboratory work for decades. Through the symmetric analysis of their action in both research, therapeutic and prevention fields, I argue that the rejection of INH chemoprophylaxis by tuberculosis experts should be understood in relation to their deeply rooted in clinical practice understanding of both biomedicine and social medicine. Firstly, I analyze the contribution of tuberculosis clinicians in the shaping of the French landscape of social medicine interventions, where BCG vaccination is already a common but fragile intervention, profoundly built-in in French health preventive policies. Secondly, I examine the way tuberculosis specialists mobilize their clinical knowledge on INH chemoprophylaxis to undermine his preventive use. Both the need to wait for a primary infection (while BCG takes place at birth) and the risk of antibioresistance make impossible for them to promote a preventive intervention which threat to compromise the efficiency of tuberculosis therapy in the future.

A new kind of doctor: Envisioning a sort of sociomedicalization in 1930s–1940s Sweden *Annika Berg, Stockholm University*

This paper will explore the shifting boundaries of medical authority in 1930s–1940s Sweden, focusing primarily on Axel Höjer's (Director-General of the Medical Board) 1948 public commission report on the future organization of out-patient medical care. In due time, Höjer's ideas on public funding and preventive healthcare would exert strong influence on Swedish healthcare organization, but when the report was published it was heavily criticized by an influential part of the Swedish medical corps. The harshest opponents warned that the reforms aimed at Soviet-style socialization – a fear that was demonstrably misguided. However, Höjer was very clear about his intentions to connect his reforms to social medicine, in the way – of several possible at the time – that he chose to define it. The period in question has been characterized as a time of biomedicalization as well as, somewhat contradictorily, a time of “sociologization” of the healthcare sector. Höjer's position points at something else. Albeit only partly realized, it very clearly aimed at an alternative kind of medicalization. Still led by doctors – but doctors of a new breed, who incorporated expertise from the emerging social sciences as well as medical expertise, thus able to integrate a broad range of “social” technologies into an expanded field of medicine and healthcare. My example shows how different and competing processes of medicalization may be going on at the same time, serving also as a more general reminder of the need for historians and STS researchers to be observant of differences within the medical corps itself.

Imbrications of Psyche and Soma within Psychosocial Medicine: Mental Health Care in the UK *Martyn Pickersgill, University of Edinburgh*

Straightforward assertions about the biomedicalisation of mental health continue to scaffold the discourse of both celebrants and critics of a (bio)medical model of mental health care. Yet, in the UK, psychosocial medicine imbricates the psyche and the soma in ways that challenge such declarations. By psychosocial medicine, I mean the care provided by medically-trained psychiatrists, as well as clinical psychologists who have an ostensibly different professional emphasis - yet who also can share much in common with psychiatry. This paper focuses primarily on a screening tool for depression called the Patient Health Questionnaire (PHQ-9). Through this, millions of citizens have come to receive a ‘score’ for their experiences of subjective

dis-ease, which in turn shapes the pharmacological and psychotherapeutic interventions that unfold from this. The PHQ-9 has helped to stabilise a major programme aimed at rolling out therapy across England to many more people than would previously have accessed it (the IAPT initiative), which has revived psychological framings of pathology and therapy. However, it has done so in ways that are more familiar within biomedical contexts. Further, the PHQ-9 exists precisely as a consequence of the psychopharmaceuticalisation of depression: it was developed through a research grant from Pfizer. By documenting these various developments, this paper contributes to re-centring questions about the place and role of psychology in contemporary healthcare. Doing so helps to complicate assumptions about the dominance of linear forms of (de)biomedicalization in health-systems, and underscores the importance of national contexts in this process

Making Psychiatry Social: Human Relations, Severe Mental Illness, and the (Bio)medicalization of Employment *Michael N. Healey, Johns Hopkins University*

Historians have long attributed the professionalization of psychiatry in the United States and Europe to the medicalization of various social issues. Inspired by previous developments in psychoanalysis and mental hygiene, the social psychiatry of the postwar period was particularly successful in this regard, gradually shifting the locus of mental healthcare away from asylums and toward the community. As they applied their expertise to interpersonal problems arising in homes, schools, workplaces, and other communal spaces, these psychiatrists aimed to foster the interdisciplinary coordination needed to address both individual and structural determinants of mental health. Collaboration with management theorists and other business stakeholders, however, influenced many to prioritize the adjustment of individuals to prevailing markets, rather than the democratization of industry or the reintegration of patients into other social spheres. While Nikolas Rose and others have described the responsabilized and optimized subjects that emerged from these and subsequent discourses, more research is needed to clarify the particular historical circumstances that directed the attention of social psychiatrists toward the productivity of their patients, especially those with severe mental illnesses. Drawing from Bruno Latour's theory of immutable mobiles, then, my paper will demonstrate how studies on vocational rehabilitation conducted by industrial psychologists of the Human Relations School shaped how social psychiatrists measured recovery from schizophrenia and related conditions, leading them to conflate mental health with re-employment and financial independence. In doing so, it aims to uncover the continuities between the medicalization facilitated by mid-century social psychiatry and the biomedicalization that characterizes mental healthcare today.

Session Organizers:

Anne Lie

Jeremy A Greene, Johns Hopkins University

Chair:

Jeremy A Greene, Johns Hopkins University

Discussant:

Nikolas Rose, Research School of Social Sciences and School of Sociology, College of Arts and Social Sciences. Aus

478. Post-Capitalist Techno-Science I: Past and Present Post-Capitalist Futures

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Under the capitalist mode of production, the world has been brought to a point of profound crisis. The present and previous centers of global empire, the U.S. and U.K., have among the highest mortality rates from the COVID-19 pandemic, while the “K-shaped recovery” exposes the profound decoupling of the pursuit of capital accumulation from that of human

welfare. Unchecked global warming threatens civilization itself while rapid ecological declines lead scientists to declare nature “under siege” (Wagner et. al. 2021). Uncritical deference to market epistemologies, combined with the industrial-scale manufacture of doubt, has resulted in crises of reproducibility and public trust in scientific findings. Meanwhile, the techno-scientific solutions power proposes point less towards a sustainable capitalism than towards increasingly baroque regimes of rentiership. Critical energies within Science and Technology Studies have often been directed against the unexamined assumptions and externalities of technoscience per se rather than the concretely-existing problems of technoscientific capitalism. Acknowledging and aiming beyond this problematic, this two-part panel takes up the urgent agenda of a post-capitalist technoscience, asking how such a project has been approached in the past and could be accomplished in the future. Bringing STS scholarship into critical theoretical and historiographic engagement with Marxism and other forms of anti-capitalist praxis, panelists will explore the problems and possibilities of scientific and technological work beyond the law of value.

Participants:

Institutions for Socialist Science in the 1960s-1970s USSR
Kulyash Zhumadilova, Virginia Tech

In my talk I will present alternatives to capitalist science and technology as practiced in the late-stage Soviet Union (1960s-1970s), often called a golden age of Soviet intellectual life. The generation of the “Sixtiers” transformed humanities and natural sciences, as well as the cultural landscape in general. I want to investigate how institutional factors such as the separation of teaching and research, incentive practices, and social norms informed knowledge production and guided the lives of ordinary scientists. I will assume a political sociology framework for my analysis, with an emphasis on institutions. My goal is to demonstrate how institutional design from a socialist standpoint informs science as a practice in terms of public outreach, human creativity, and the formation of research questions. For example, I will look at formation and infrastructure of “naukograds” or “science cities”, towns with high concentration of research centers. I draw on historical literature from the period (memoirs, program documents, etc.) and contemporary reflections on non-capitalist modes of doing science.

Revisiting History, Reenvisioning Science: The Search for Alternatives and the Role of Activist STS
Sigrud Schmalzer, Professor, University of Massachusetts Amherst

In the 1970s and 1980s, scientists and STS scholars in the US organization Science for the People (SfP) generated radical critiques of science as practiced under capitalism. Among many endeavors, SfP sent delegates to the People’s Republic of China in 1973; the next year they published a celebratory book, *China: Science Walks on Two Legs*. For SfP, socialist China represented an inspiring alternative—in its recognition of the class politics of knowledge; its mobilization of workers, women, and others marginalized by capitalist science; and above all its pursuit of science and technology for the benefit of the people rather than for corporate profit or global domination. In 2019, some members of the recently revitalized SfP proposed to republish the 1974 book. The suggestion provoked a lively discussion within the group about the legitimacy of Chinese socialism under Mao and the degree to which the delegates (all white Americans) understood what they saw. In response, a few members volunteered to organize a critical edition of the book (a project now underway) with analysis by members of the original delegation along with STS scholars. Based on historical research and participation in the recent events described above, the speaker will explore possibilities and problematics in the search for radical science alternatives—and how activist STS scholars can participate effectively in this process.

Red and Expert: Overcoming the Opposition Between Head and Hand
Josh Lalonde

Expertise is an inherently inequalitarian concept: if someone is an expert, others must not be experts. There is therefore a conflict or

tension between the role of the expert and egalitarian political projects such as communism. I will examine two cases in which this tension reached a crisis level, namely in the Soviet Union from 1928 to 1931 and in the Cultural Revolution in China roughly from 1967 to 1976. In each case, the party leadership pursued a multi-pronged strategy to reduce and eventually eliminate the opposition between intellectual and manual labour, or “head” and “hand”. First, access to education was dramatically expanded at all levels; second, the content taught in educational institutions was reformed so as to emphasize the practical rather than the theoretical; and finally, the political and economic privileges of non-communist “bourgeois” experts were attacked, sometimes violently. In both cases, however, this strategy ultimately failed, as the attempt to overcome the opposition between head and hand had the paradoxical effect of reinforcing that very distinction and entrenching the power of a new stratum of “red” experts. I conclude by suggesting that future egalitarian political projects must concern themselves not only with eliminating the class power of experts inherited from the old society, but also with preventing the formation of new class inequalities based on expertise.

Session Organizers:

Owen Marshall

Helena Sheehan, Dublin City University

479. Infrastructuring Research: (Re)assembling Collaboration and Place-Making Practices I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Research infrastructures (RIs) are typically understood as – either centralized or distributed - material, organizational and regulatory formations that aim to facilitate scientific practice in specific domains. While often treated as relatively durable and invisible underpinnings of technoscientific endeavours, the importance of RIs in facilitating large-scale scientific initiatives have recently become increasingly prominent. This panel addresses how the ‘infrastructuring’ of research – i.e. the planning, construction, operation, and maintenance of RIs – provides a key site for studying how collaboration and particular understandings of place (in relation to e.g. identity) are assembled. We consider infrastructuring processes not only in terms of the sociomaterial formation of infrastructures, but explicitly include symbolic and narrative processes that contribute to the solidity – as well as transformations - of RIs across space and time. Across the sessions, we ask: Which kinds of research activities are included and excluded from infrastructuring processes? How do political and economic dimensions of (especially cross-national) collaboration feature in infrastructuring? What are the implications of infrastructure for how research is practiced, funded, and evaluated? How is the location (or distribution across locations) of RIs perceived in relation to the character of scientific work? How do spatial boundaries of RIs relate to imaginations of their social, political, and cultural ‘location’? Which kinds of identities are formed, transformed, or rejected through the formation of RIs? Which narratives are mobilized to make infrastructures and collaboration work, and conversely, how are these narratives shaped by prior histories of infrastructuring and collaborating?

Participants:

Infrastructuring as community-building: Early-Career Researchers at CERN
Helene Sorgner, Alpen-Adria-Universität Klagenfurt | Wien | Graz

In this talk, I analyze how early career-researchers in experimental particle physics engage in infrastructuring as a means of building individual and collective identities and futures. As the paradigmatic case of “big science”, particle physics research traditionally organizes around large research infrastructures. Today, a majority of the international research community is involved in one of the experiments run at the Large Hadron Collider (LHC) at CERN. More than half of the researchers working on the LHC experiments are early-career researchers (PhD students and post-docs) on temporary contracts.

Employing a broad notion of “infrastructuring”, I argue that early-career researchers engage in material, social, and symbolic infrastructuring processes, which both shape and are informed by their idea of what it means to be a particle physicist. They contribute to the upgrading and maintenance of technical infrastructures as part of forming a professional identity. They build a social infrastructure of networking events, resources and advocacy to foster a more supportive and egalitarian research environment. As of recently, early-career researchers also engage in community-wide discussions about future infrastructures. In their contribution to the European Strategy Update for particle physics (2020), a delegation of 180 early-career researchers explicitly related questions about future colliders to the future of the community, demanding that particle physics research become more socially inclusive and ecologically sustainable. Based on this report and interviews with early-career researchers working at the LHC, I show how they engage in infrastructuring to build a research community that fosters more diverse and sustainable identities and careers.

Rocket Politics: European space infrastructures in the New Space Age *Nina Klimburg Witjes, Vienna University*

Large-scale and highly visible infrastructures play a strong symbolic role in connecting different regions, supporting the narratives of a united Europe made through shared infrastructural projects. In this paper, I explore how rocket infrastructures contribute to the making of Europe and how practices of infrastructural collectivity are linked to rationales of political connectivity. Focusing on the European rocket Ariane, often presented as a symbol of European integration, I ask how it shapes and is being shaped by processes of European infrastructural integration: 20 years after World War 2, European countries began to explore the opportunities for a collaboratively built launch vehicle, called “Europa”. However, it lacked a shared set of ideas of what a European space program should be about and never fully launched. With the foundation of the European Space Agency in 1975, a new rocket, Ariane 1, was built and became for decades the most successful on the market. However, as the commercial New Space Age flourishes, the European collaboration model is not competitive with private companies such as SpaceX. Ariane 6, the newest version, continually spurs controversies in the European space sector about the need to maintain such an expensive large-scale infrastructure and its contribution to so-called European autonomy. Mobilizing work in STS and infrastructure studies, I attend to practices of infrastructuring as relational to space-making practices, forms of European (dis)integration, and sovereignty and trace how collective space infrastructures help stabilize notions of Europe and, conversely, how imaginaries of Europe materialize in these large-scale space infrastructures.

CERN’s Detectors as Layered Infrastructures for International Collaboration *Kamiel Mobach, University of Vienna*

Detectors built and operated at the European Organization for Nuclear Research (CERN), from the 1980s onwards, have become prime examples of large international collaboration. They are large in terms of size, number of people involved, and amount of money spent. In addition, they are complex in terms of the diversity of technologies that must come together smoothly, the variety of international experts gathered, and the globally dispersed production chains involved. Reaching this size and complexity also requires the alignment of disparate elements such as intercontinental money flows, different organizational cultures, and competing experimental traditions. How could these elements successfully come together in a detector and become stabilized? How did these processes of integration change the elements that were brought together and create a whole that lived up to initial expectations? Using document analyses and interviews, this talk outlines how CERN’s detectors became centerpieces in the intercontinental integration of particle physics. This integration has been a heterogeneous, layered

process: different types of elements needed to be brought together, in different subsystems, and these subsystems needed to be coordinated to form a coherently working detector. This analysis will also show that next to the planning, construction and alignment of different material structures, the articulation of shared future visions such as research goals was needed, as well as a performance of disregarding geopolitics, while implicitly acknowledging the industrial and political importance of technoscience. This process (re)shaped institutional identities and brought to life infrastructures that have been durable beyond single detectors.

Understanding the Science-Politics Interfaces of European Big Science in the 20th and 21st Century *Katharina Cramer, University of Bonn*

This contribution explores how multilateral scientific collaboration in Europe is shaped by and within political contexts. More concretely, it illustrates how national research priorities, science budgets, long-term commitments and local site selection processes were treated in highly political contexts. On the one hand, although large-scale research facilities are international in their conceptualization, they are sensitive to the specific local conditions: With massive technological centerpieces – accelerators, beam lines, detectors – that are unable to move or to travel, they are geographically identifiable locations where scientists, technologies and politics are co-located. On the other hand, a complex net of actors situated between science and politics – scientists and administrators, government representatives and politicians – constitutes the various enabling conditions for the establishment, implementation and construction of such projects. Hence, the establishment and operation of large-scale research projects can only be fully understood by combining the analysis of science policy strategies at different levels – from the local to the international – with insights into specific discursive and organizational dynamics. This contribution is based on two case studies: the European Synchrotron Radiation Facility (ESRF) located in Grenoble, France and the European X-Ray Free Electron Laser (XFEL) located in Hamburg, Germany. It analyses decisive events in the history of two European Big Science facilities contributing to a more detailed understanding of intergovernmental scientific cooperation in Europe in the late 20th century and early 21st century.

Minor Infrastructures in/for the Anthropocene. How might research infrastructures to study planetary transformations be reconfigured to account for significant differences? *Jörg Niewöhner, Humboldt-Universität zu Berlin*

Global research infrastructures that address planetary environmental change are undergoing rapid change. What started with global circulation models to better understand climate change itself moved towards integrated assessment models to better understand socio-economic option spaces in relation to a changing climate and is now arriving at a panoply of attempts to better understand the coevolution of material and social dynamics across scales. While increasingly diversifying, these research infrastructures retain a shared Western ontology that divides nature and culture into entities interacting within systems. Epistemologically, it is driven by data understood as representations that can be aggregated and integrated in order to generalise statistically across spatial scales and time. Methodologically, numerical modelling and computer simulations are integrated and coupled to address the planetary dimension. International consortia, first and foremost the IPCC, form the organisational backbone of these infrastructures. This contribution discusses whether these global research infrastructures can be and indeed ought to be turned minor. Minor infrastructures in the Deleuzian sense refer to infrastructures that have not only inscribed into them and do not only afford a single late liberal, modern cosmology. Rather minor

infrastructures enable those concerned by the work that these infrastructures do to appropriate their operations and outcomes for their own purposes. Building on discussions about the possibility to reconnect global climate change research to local experiences, I suggest here that we ought to address not only the outcomes of research but engage with the practices and models themselves. Situated modelling and agonistic integration are suggested as one way of provincialising and making minor current infrastructures in order to account for significant differences in cosmology/ontology, expertise and experiences of planetary change.

Session Organizers:

Nina Klimburg Witjes, Vienna University
Erik Aarden, Alpen-Adria University Klagenfurt
Kamiel Mobach, University of Vienna
Oguz Özkan, MCTS Technical University Munich
Zinaida Vasilyeva, MCTS, TU München
Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies
Sebastian Michael Pfothner, Technical University Munich

Discussants:

Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies
Sebastian Michael Pfothner, Technical University Munich

480. Soil Sensing: Methods, politics and experience - II: Sensing toxicity and remediation

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

Participants:

From Brownfield to Green Urban Nature: Unearthing the 'Black Box' of Soil Pollution in the Tel Aviv Metropolitan Region *Uri Ansenberg, School of Sustainability, Interdisciplinary Center Herzliya; Nathan Marom, School of Sustainability, IDC Herzliya*

The paper examines soil rehabilitation plans for three military-industry contaminated sites located in the Tel-Aviv metropolitan region. In all three sites, the excessive soil remediation costs are intended to be financed by revenues from large-scale lucrative real-estate projects planned on the polluted ground. The paper thus addresses the techno-scientific and political-economic relationships between the contaminated soil and the planning processes and argues that the socio-material relations between the soil contamination and urban plans are responsible for their simultaneous co-production. The co-production process of urban plans and soil-contamination is explored through the prism of Actor-Network Theory (ANT). Typical to ANT, our investigation focuses on the field's inherent controversies with a specific focus on a dispute whether or not the soil contamination should be fully investigated and mapped prior to the planning process. The focus on this and other controversies highlights and transcribes the field's social and policy debates, without recourse to predetermined conceptual assumptions and methodological protocols. Allowing the actors themselves to serve as our investigators, we are thus able to unearth the 'black box' of soil pollution in urban planning. We discover not only that the plans and the contamination are co-produced, but also that the contamination is actively responsible for the production of urban green natures, as well as civic engagement and environmental protest to protect this "nature". Thus, our case stands as a counterpoint to the common argument that the production of the urban environment is at odds with the natural environment.

From Failed Wetlands to Biodiscovery and Bioremediation:

Technopolitics of Fungi Restoration at the Jackpile Uranium Mine in Laguna Pueblo, New Mexico, U.S. *Thomas De Pree, University of New Mexico Health Sciences Center*

Since the emergence of the scientific paradigm of geomicrobiology as a specialized field in the 1980s (Erich and Newman 2009), the applied sciences and engineering of "microbial reduction of uranium" would become one of the leading communities of thought and practice (see Lovely et al. 1991). In the United States, the Department of Energy spent millions of dollars on environmental remediation methods using cultures of bacteria at abandoned uranium mines (AUMs). Acknowledging the limitations of past remediation methods, and a legacy of failed wetland restoration projects, contemporary Superfund research scientists are reluctant to overstate the promise of microbiological and abiological reduction of soluble and oxidized uranium, but they have advanced new methods of biodiscovery and bioremediation. Thinking with the concept of "geontologies" (Povinelli 2016:5), this paper will examine novel applications of biogeochemistry and geomicrobiology in monitoring and restoring AUMs through "engaged anthropology" (Kirsch 2018). Based on two years of multi-locale ethnographic research (2017- 2019), and six months of collaborative work in the Community Engagement Core of the METALS Superfund Research Center at the University of New Mexico, this paper portrays my collaboration with the environmental and biomedical research projects, and community partners in Laguna Pueblo and the Navajo Nation, and our process of co-designing "interventions" to attenuate environmental health risks and impacts. This is the beginning of a multi-species ethnography of geomicrobiology and ethnomycology, and an examination of the technopolitics of biomonitoring and bioremediation at AUMs in Indigenous lands in the North American Southwest.

Soil and water or soilwater? How a knowledge controversy muddles participation in the Netherlands *Marieke Meesters*

In this article, we analyse how the impacts of mining are understood, enacted and addressed. We also present an analysis of how causality is claimed, substantiated, and contested. In the context of mining, causality and causal claims play an important role in public disputes. This article draws on studies of material participation, Indigenous scholarship and decolonial posthuman theory, in particular Karen Barad's agential realism framework. We offer a detailed empirical analysis that focuses on the role of measurement practices; how they enact the boundaries of and between objects, contribute to the establishment of causal claims and the constitution of issues, and shape participatory processes. Our analysis presents human and non-human bodies as something inherently malleable. This malleability matters, because measurement devices have been associated with political agendas that steer towards neoliberal ends and that celebrate economic gains, often at the expense of other societal values. Following recent contributions on response-abilities in posthuman worlds we aim to mobilize our analysis not just to describe these practices and their implications, but also reflect on what alternative issues and objects could have been enacted. We conclude with alternatives for how measurements can be employed to foreground values of democracy, justice, and care.

The Social Life of Sediment: Vulnerability and Disaster Waste Management in the Aftermath of the 2018 Montecito Debris Flow *Summer Gray, University of California, Santa Barbara*

The catastrophic convergence of drought, wildfire, and extreme weather that culminated in a series of deadly debris flows that wiped out a large portion of the wealthy enclave of Montecito, California in 2018, expose a complex interplay of biophysical hazards, infrastructural instabilities, and uneven social vulnerabilities. From the invisible maintenance of tourist shores and wealthy river basins to the dumping of toxic mud on the beaches of the poor, this paper critically examines the role that disaster recovery plays in shifting vulnerability from highly valued areas to those that are deemed less desirable. Drawing on qualitative research and 25 in-depth interviews with residents and experts conducted in the aftermath of the debris flow, this paper

provides a social analysis of the multifaceted ways in which disaster waste management is involved in transfers of vulnerability from the wildland-urban interface to the intertidal zone. It follows the interconnected social and physical processes of sediment buildup and landslide fallout against a backdrop of existing efforts to maintain geographies of affluence and spatial inequality. It also highlights tensions between experts and victims regarding the usage of the scientific term “debris flow,” which some residents have rejected on the basis that it fails to capture the visceral realities of the hazard it aims to describe.

Viviez (France) and Estarreja (Portugal): Two Municipalities Faced with the Toxic Legacy of Industrial Residues Trapped in their Soils *christelle gramaglia, UMR GEAU INRAE; Sofia Bento, Lisbon School of Economics and Management; Lucia Fernandes, University of Coimbra*

In Estarreja (Portugal) and Viviez/Decazeville (France), past industrial activities have generated significant soil and water pollution. The presence of large slag heaps and slag heaps, unevenly cleaned and made safe, bears witness to this. These large deposits of coarse matter give food for thought about the quantities of metals and organic pollutants which, in the form of small residues may have been disseminated in the environment, notably by infiltrating the soil and contaminating the groundwater and rivers. Our communication is based on a comparative survey carried out in France and Portugal, in municipalities where mobilization against pollution has never been strong, whereas they have become real laboratory sites for specialists in environmental chemistry and health. Inspired by recent STS research on the underground, it focuses on the subterranean fate of industrial pollution - and questions the conditions of its resurgence in the local public space. We report more particularly on the controversies that have accompanied the metrological efforts made to try to characterise and quantify these pollutions. We also discuss the way in which the two municipalities concerned have positioned themselves, either to put the question of industrial residues trapped in the underground back on the political agenda, or on the contrary, to deal with it from a purely technical angle. Our communication shows that these approaches give rise to different strategies for managing the risks and considering the rehabilitation of the soils. It discusses the conditions of a governance that would no longer be residual, but rather precautionary.

Session Organizer:

Abby Kinchy, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Chair:

Daniel Walls, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Discussant:

Sebastian Ureta, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

481. Total Institutions: Technosciences of Care and Control II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Erving Goffman (1961) called both prisons and psychiatric wards “total institutions,” gesturing to the intertwined nature of care, capture, and control in efforts to manage deviance of the soul, psyche, or self. This panel investigates institutions and techniques of mental health care in the Global North, South, and colonial contexts, grappling with the criminological, forensic, pastoral and penal impulses of the psy-disciplines. Building from the work of feminist science and technology studies, abolitionist scholarship (Wang 2018), studies of racial capitalism (Robinson 1983), and historical and sociological studies of psychiatry, social services, and the prison industrial complex (Roberts 2001, Metzl 2010, Ryan Hatch 2019, Raz 2020, Smith 2020), panelists will explore the connective tissue between the prison and the asylum, probing the practices, histories, expertise and apparatuses within the mental health care professions and other social services (from psychiatry, psychology, psychotherapy, and beyond) that knit together the carceral with the biomedical.

Participants:

Among biomedicine, therapeutics, quotas and other non-humans: enactings on behavior-related diagnosis in scholar context with Intercultural-Bilingual Education Program *Natalia Hirmas Montecinos, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile*

Access to detection and therapeutic services on behavior-related diagnosis in school contexts has been envisioned as a step towards equity and social justice, especially for historically marginalized groups. Nevertheless, historical records on the colonial uses of western medical and school practices, along with the current alarming disproportionality of original people children in diagnoses of school origin (special educational needs), leads us to problematize the presence of logics beyond therapeutics and education, in a place that has become one of the main starting sites for psychiatric diagnoses of children and young people today: schools. While the enactments of psy-disciplines in the management of deviance and its problematic effects have been mostly researched in traditionally related to mental health care settings (asylums, prisons, and newly, community mental health services), this presentation will delve into the diversity of human and non-human actants, and processes of (de)enrollment involved in the enactings of behavioral-related diagnoses carried out in a school with Intercultural-Bilingual Education Program - particularly stressed by the state mandate to revitalize the indigenous. School does. From social studies of diagnosis, and through an ethnographic work oriented from the actor-network theory (ANT), the results provide an approach towards heterogeneous assemblages where biomedical nosologies are mixed with legal decrees, temporalities, forms, quotas, facial gestures, childhood and civilizational progress myths - all of which, entangled, constitute new oppressive networks through diagnostic neocolonial stakes, requiring the summoning of more sophisticated approaches towards equity and justice.

Ethnography Inside Out: The Case of the Occupied Clinic *Saiba Varma, University of California San Diego*

What happens to care under conditions of violence and occupation? How do we analytically separate care from violence? Taking these questions as a starting point, this paper examines the co-implications of carceral and biomedical regimes in Indian-controlled Kashmir, one of the most militarized places in the world. Drawing on methods borrowed from feminist and decolonial STS, it asks how theorizing care and violence together force new methodological turns--such as the notion of 'inside out' ethnography, a concept that refers to a reversal of normative separations between ethnographic object and 'background' or 'context.' Through inside-out ethnography, this paper situates the clinic not as a standalone or discrete object, but rather, as a space contiguous with other sources and spaces of harm and violence in the region.

Mental Health Chatbots at Work *Valerie Black, UC Berkeley*

Mental Health chatbots aren't exactly new—think Weizenbaum's ELIZA and Colby's PARRY. Yet within the past 5 years, chatbots have seamlessly transitioned into the space of standard workplace health benefits. What factors account for this change? I argue that the answer to this question is more complicated and nuanced than simply 'increased access to smartphones.' This paper examines the role of ubiquitous yet curiously opaque Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs) in dramatically expanding the reach of chatbot care. As third-party companies contracted to provide care services to workplaces, EAPs have come to vitally sustain the major players in the burgeoning industry of mental health chatbot startups via a business-to-business model of consumption. But what exactly do EAPs seek from chatbots, and what in turn do workplaces, as clients of EAPs, expect of this ultramodern-yet-retro approach? Drawing on eighteen months of ethnographic fieldwork conducted at a

Silicon Valley mental health chatbot startup, this paper opens up the relationship between EAPs and chatbot makers, while investigating how monitoring and response to suicide ideation creates a space of ethically fraught exception to EAP policy around workplace privacy. The path of therapeutic chatbots is still unfolding; but they are swiftly becoming institutionalized in a pattern that leaves workers vulnerable to unspecified surveillance via care. This anthropological and disability studies-informed approach shows how even with “old-school” modes of AI, the formation of adequate and comprehensive ethical frameworks remains unsettlingly open-ended.

Unbecoming Objects: A Critique of Racial & Psychiatric Reason *Eric Reinhart, Harvard University*

This paper returns to Sylvia Wynter's critique of the modern representational regime subtending the claims of "man," positing intertwined racial and psychiatric rationality as cornerstones of this deterritorialized total institution. To this end, I invoke fragments of an ethnography of self-writing as subversive act in Chicago's racialized neighborhoods—long rendered the "laboratory" for urban sociology and its discourses of pathology—and carceral institutions, interweaving these with a deconstructive account of the discourses of race and reason by which the subject as such must be named, policed, diagnosed, and punished. The paper thus takes ethnographic relationships as both enveloped within and subversive of their overdetermining symbolic coordinates, problematizing the compulsion to speak and write oneself from positions of constitutive exclusion. I argue that the inherent failure to carry out this impossible task is both an effect of oppressive power and a privileged opening to other forms of being, feeling, and communality.

Session Organizer:

Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley

Chair:

Beth Semel, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

482. Data (Dis)trust In The Global South: The Case Of Covid-19 – II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

What kinds of data have we produced at the local, national or transnational scale to deal and respond to Covid-19? Over the past year we have grown accustomed to measure, quantify, report, visualize, and account for all aspects of our lives. This has also come with a growing need for “valid” data and what it means to produce, share, circulate, and trust it. The assumption that data, especially more data, will lead to societal betterment is one that tends to pervade both academic conversations in data studies and public discourse. We do not argue against the importance of generating data in the face of local and global problems. Rather, we seek to challenge the assumption that critical analysis of, and intervention into, data infrastructures should happen primarily at the stage of data production. In conversation with citizen science studies the panel argues that data distrust must be taken as an integral part of data infrastructures and capacities—particularly in the context of the global south. This intervention is relevant in that it seeks to destabilize a globally adopted dichotomy that pits people who reject scientific findings against other forms of knowledge. It builds on the contention that data (dis)trust is not a “cultural” attitude of the public, but rather the result of situated processes through which frustration, uncertainty, and cynicism are enacted and produced. We are interested in understanding how data distrust—particularly around health and Covid-19—is produced and mobilized within various and transnational social fields and institutional settings.

Participants:

Covid-19 Deaths in Rural Colombia. ‘SARS Associated to the Pandemic’ as a Diagnosis at the Margins of the State *Julia Morales Fontanilla, Rutgers University - New Jersey, USA*
Covid-19 emerged as a local health crisis in Colombia amid a humanitarian migration and refugee emergency and in the context of a decades old landscape of extreme violence,

dispossession, social disparities, and disproportionate state abandonment. As in many other public health scenarios at different scales globally, in Colombia the Covid-19 pandemic brought to the fore how structural inequity and the precarity of state governing organize who gets access to diagnostic technoscience and biomedical treatments, and, subsequently, who counts as a Covid-19 case (or not) in the country. This situation allowed for the emergence of a local tension around Covid-19 diagnosing and official data. A tension that is also present after death. In this paper I think with the politics of death and interrogate how deaths officially become Covid-19 related (or not) in a small hospital in rural Colombia. Out of fieldwork with local forensic workers and a forensic pathologist at the rural hospital's morgue, I provide an account of how morgue workers search for causes of death during an autopsy, what they do when they find lethal anatomies indicative of a Covid-19 diagnosis, and how their findings confront official data. I conceptualize the diagnostic solution they offer —‘SARS associated to the pandemic’— as indicative of the doctor's resourcefulness, state abandonment, the particularities of making diagnosis of a viral disease after death, and the complexities of a totally new biomedical diagnosis. This work contributes to current conversation on the global south and STS, biomedical knowledge, and the Covid-19 pandemic.

Beyond COVID-19 Data Infrastructure in Ecuador *Fu Yu Chang, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*

Since the start of the pandemic, data collection has played a key role in learning about the disease and the efforts to control it. Epidemiologists around the world were building their knowledge based on statistical numbers of contagion, transmission, and deaths caused by the SARS-CoV-2 virus. Ecuador's COVID-19 data was collected by a national digital platform managed by the Ministry of Health. This data was officially released and made public by the government on a daily basis. Now, the same set of data was interpreted very differently depending on who used the numbers and what they used them for. For instance, the low number of cases in rural areas was interpreted by many as a success in limiting the spread of COVID-19. But, for health professionals working in those same places it meant that we just didn't have enough resources to test the population. Science and Technology Studies (STS) tell us that infrastructure is never neutral. Numbers don't always tell the truth, we need to see beyond bare numbers and be critical about their multiple meanings and the ways in which they are produced. What does Ecuador's digital infrastructure and the data it produces tell us about health governance? How does the data shape our knowledge of COVID-19 and influence our behavior? In this piece I ethnographically approach the ways in which Ecuador's health system's digital infrastructure worked during the first 10 months of the pandemic in order to understand how COVID-19 data was produced locally, how it determined the country's ill response, and why distrust in data is commonplace among the population.

Classification, Enumeration and Evidence: Leprosy and Covid-19 in Brazil *Glauca Maricato, Free University of Berlin*

The Covid-19 pandemic has prompted an intense circulation of tables, graphics and statistics, as well as it has brought terms such as “epidemic curve” and “exponential growth” into our routines. Such numerical narratives have been at the center of disputes and negotiations over the power to describe local epidemiological realities. The attention has not been solely placed on the numbers (percentages, etc.), but on the relation between them. How many new cases have been reported? How many deaths? How old were those who died? How many people were tested? How many in other countries? Over the past nine years I have been researching on the ongoing campaigns to eliminate leprosy (also known as Hansen's disease) as a public health problem. More recently, I have been trying to demonstrate how early 1990's global shift in the way leprosy cases were to be classified and enumerated was

decisive to the World Health Organization's (WHO) declaration that leprosy was eliminated by the early 2000s'. Drawing on STS literature and based on ethnographic research in Brazil (pointed by WHO as the only country in the world that has now yet eliminated leprosy), this paper reflects on the ontological politics of leprosy elimination. By doing so, it intends to put in parallel the 'numerical narratives of control' surrounding the so-called "oldest disease" (leprosy) and one of the newest ones (Covid-19) and contribute to debates on how (un)certainities and (dis)trust are coproduced by situated entanglements (between statistics, political crisis, biological elements, knowledge hierarchies, etc.).

Session Organizer:

Sofia Carpio, Kaleidos Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

Chair:

Mayra Alejandra Flores, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

Discussant:

Jorge Nunez, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

483. Ferment as Method: Creating the Conditions for Transformative Relations - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Where the 2020 pandemic prompted new desires for hyper-sterile environments, it also sparked interest in the microbe-rich world of fermentation. Home kitchens, wiped clean with bleach and sanitizer, produced effervescent brews, doubling sourdoughs, and funky sauerkrauts. Fermentation provided a collaborative 'contamination' (Tsing 2015) that prompted experimentation, care, and new forms of sustenance amid loss, isolation, and precarity. In fermentation microbes transform their substrates and each other into new forms, textures, flavors, aromas, and matters. Practicing fermentation invites open-ended collaboration across species boundaries; requiring attention (when is it ferment and when is it rot?), care (who needs more water, more food, more salt?), and a willingness for all parties to be changed by the process (no one is coming out the same as they went in) (Fournier 2020, Maroney 2018, Villalba 2019). Fermentation is more than a material process; ideas, people, and movements ferment. The concept offers a rich metaphor that captures the energy of activists, and transformative potential at any scale. Since ferments can also turn sour, go awry, become toxic, and foment violence and trouble, as a metaphor for responsible change, it contains its own limits. This panel invites participants to ferment as a method in their STS projects. How does thinking with fermentation foreground new configurations of interdependence and care in our work? How might a slower process that allows for unexpected results affect our means of producing knowledge? Might such a method, emergent in the becoming together, open up space to foster 'good' relations or challenge 'bad' ones?

Participants:

A Mingling of Milk and Birch: Fermentation Vessels and the Topologies of Containment *Tyler Adkins, Princeton University*

Based on twenty months of participant ethnography, this paper critically examines the notion of "container" from the vantage point of the Indigenous Altai People of Southern Siberia. Especially in the current moment, Euro-American conceptions of containers and containment emphasize a hermetic, immunological separation between the contained and the environment: modern containers— from plastic bottles to the walls of office buildings— are supposed to be impermeable, non-reactive, and minimally intrusive. In contrast, the containers valued in Altai dairying and fermentation practices — from birch barrels, to cured-leather sacks, to smoked sheep bladders— are supposed to have a reactive and transformative relationship to their contents. Altai milk fermentation barrels, for instance, are not only made to be maximally hospitable to fermentative

organisms, but are also made to mediate, rather than entirely intervene, between its contents and the oxygen and moisture in the outside atmosphere. Working from Altai fermentation vessels as a site to reimagine the meanings and ethics of containment, this paper provides an ethnographically grounded critique of our immunological conceptions of container, contained, and environment.

Effervescence At The Edges: Contours Of The Political In The Containers Of Fermentation

Anuj Vaidya

In this paper, I wish to consider the role of the container in shaping ferments – both as the form that holds the process of fermentation, and also as the limit that allows fermentation to occur, to collapse, and sometimes even to explode. The very materiality of the container (earthen-ware and glass, plastics, recycled mason jars and jam bottles) is a matter of concern; as is the recipe that inhabits the container. It is the strength of the relations between the various ingredients of the ferment that will produce the effervescence to be negotiated at the edge of the container, letting it seep out into the world, or dive back into the space of queer (un)becoming. Ultimately, for me, this concern with containers offers the possibility to think about effervescence in a political context, especially in relation to community and activism in the aftermath of the COVID pandemic and the Black Lives Matter movement. What lessons and insights can be gained from tracing social movements against the process of fermentation? In this paper, I put my own participation in solidarity building and local citizen activism networks in Davis, CA into conversation with fermentation to see what cross-pollinates, and what hybrid insights I can take back to both activism and to fermentation. This is not using fermentation as untethered metaphor, rather it is about thinking through the possibilities and the limits of this metaphor, by paying due attention to the materials and methods that make fermentation possible.

Fervent Manifesto: Interrupted Practices

Mercedes P Villalba, Department of Anthropology, UC Davis

This talk explores ways in which creative time dialogues with crisis time, looking at some of the strategies of publication and creation that emerge from navigating a temporary or permanent lack of "free" time. What do strategies of independent publishing, guerrilla printing, zine-making, note-taking, interrupted writing, tell us about creating in states of precarity? What is the genealogy of expecting creative time to only be possible from an excess of leisure time? I start from a text I wrote in my kitchen table in 2016, called fervent manifesto. I wrote that text in short rushes, stealing bits of time from more pressing tasks, out of a sense of urgency and under the pressure of a deadline I had pushed too many times already. This state, an already common writing practice for many, is becoming even more standardized as the emergency measures taken during 2020 to account for new labor conditions under a pandemic, are being normalized into new, long-term, work practices. Trying to acknowledge the fact that the fantasies I have about writing are far from what I usually find myself doing, I explore the origins of this dissonance in the genealogy of the fantasies of "the writer" and in the fruitful and robust archive of writers, makers and artists who have created outside of the abundant time of privilege. On the archive of disruptive practices, fermentation acts as both a metaphor and a practice that helps me re-orient my expectations of what normal time is, and what failing at something means.

Making The Relay: Microbial Relations and the Hyphenated Practices of Fermentation

Maya Hey, Concordia University (Montreal, CANADA)

What does it mean to have 'good' relations with microbial life? As a historically situated practice, fermentation offers new configurations of care, arranging us differently than the anthropocentric assumption of vertical control. Importantly,

fermentation does not guarantee cooperation or known outcomes, necessitating practices that are adaptive, pluripotent, and able to respond. This paper argues that the material practices of fermentation provide ways of relating to microbial life without overdetermining what microbes are (e.g. probiotic, pathogenic) or how we ought to live with them (e.g. commensalism, instrumentalism). It argues that fermentation as method offers the possibility of transformation without pre-settling what actants are or do. Based on ethnographic fieldwork in several breweries and creameries in Japan, this paper examines two practices that thematically reoccur in fermentation: space-making and attunement. In instances of spontaneous fermentation, space-making adopts elements of inclusive design so that the ferment can invite a diverse array of species. Attunement orients and activate human bodies in multispecies, multisensorial epistemologies. Notably, these are hyphenated practices wherein human-and-microbe act as a composite participant. At the core of these practices are emplaced and embodied senses of self, which, arguably, we-humans could translate into other arenas such as 'kitchens', 'laboratories', and 'fields'. This paper challenges the narrative of fermentation that centers a human instigator by focusing on hyphenated practices that acknowledge the enmeshed and co-constituted nature of human-and-microbe. In doing so, this paper offers a more complex tool for STS, going beyond the 'human' or 'microbe' as singular units of agency.

Thickening Descriptions: on the (im)possibility of ethnography while the milk curdles *Matthaeus Rest, MPI for evolutionary Anthropology*

In most Alpine cheese recipes, it takes 35 min for the milk to curdle. In theory, this sounds like the perfect amount of time to sit down with the cheesemaker, have a cup of coffee and talk about their practice of making cheese in the mountain summer pastures, their care for microbes, animals, pastures and themselves. In reality, there is never time for this. Once the rennet is added, the cheesemaker will start washing wheels in the aging room, the veterinary arrives in just then and wants to know which cow she has to treat or inseminate, or suddenly the shepherds come running and need help mending a fence before the whole herd escapes. For my ethnography of peasant dairying, it turned out that revisits in the winter were necessary when I often conducted very conventional interviews. This lack of time in artisanal dairy fermentation stands in stark contrast to the 'leisure fermentation' that has become so influential over the past years and especially the pandemic lockdowns. The main reason for my dairy ethnography emerges from a very different engagement with time: my collaboration with a group of biomolecular archaeologists. Through traces of ancient DNA and proteins, they aim to understand the prehistoric spread of dairying. But in order to understand their ancient samples, they need contemporary dairy microbes from non-industrial contexts. In some sense, they thereby render present-day dairy farmers and their microbes living fossils. These temporal contradictions will be the focus of my talk.

Session Organizer:

Susannah Chapman, School of Social Science, The University of Queensland

Chair:

Stephanie Maroney, University of California, Davis

484. Governing Environmental Inequalities: Towards a New Research-Action Framework on Agency, Power & Multispecies Justice – I: Agents, Power & Agency

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:

The Symmetry Principle and the Justice Agenda *Ingemar Bohlin, University of Gothenburg, Dpt of Philosophy,*

Linguistics & Theory of Science

The principle of symmetry is often described as central to constructivist STS. When introduced in the 1970s, it was disputed not only by rationalist philosophers, but also by proponents of the radical science movement. Since then, this tension between political and epistemological radicalism has generated numerous disputes within STS. Over several decades, independently of developments in STS, social justice has emerged as an important theme in many social-scientific disciplines. Academic specialties have sprung up around topics such as environmental, health, and educational justice, and concepts such as epistemic injustice are frequently cited. There are strong affinities between long-standing STS concerns and justice-oriented scholarship and activism, and in recent years the justice agenda has been widely adopted in STS, too. The aim of this paper is to shed light on the relationship between justice-oriented STS and symmetry. Given that methodological symmetry does not amount to political neutrality, the symmetrical style of analysis might be used to support communities who are being treated unfairly. Is symmetry in fact adopted for that purpose in justice-oriented STS, or is the identification of injustice incompatible with the methodological principle of avoiding committing oneself to the well-foundedness or otherwise of the knowledge claims addressed in a study? Put briefly, does the relationship between symmetry and the justice agenda of current STS reproduce the one between SSK and science critics in the 1970s, or is the present situation a different one?

Address climate change vulnerability – does caste matter?

Hema Vaishnavi Ale, Transitions Research

Climate change impacts vulnerabilities differentially across the social strata, and in a South Asian context, impacts on the lower castes are likely to be disproportionately high. The role of caste in understanding vulnerability to climate change, however, remains largely unexamined. With the increasing occurrence of extreme weather events associated with climate change, social vulnerabilities need to be understood for addressing disaster risk reduction and coping mechanisms. Looking at caste as a technoscientific field helps understand how historical vulnerabilities and intersectionalities are sustained and reinforced through governance mechanisms and social networks. The knowledge of climate change and its impacts on their everyday lives itself influences these vulnerabilities, which could be explored by examining the complex issues of power, knowledge and decision-making within climate governance and its implications on the most marginalised. By looking at three extreme weather events, the 2015 heatwave, Cyclone Fani and Cyclone Titli, which impacted the Andhra Pradesh and Telangana regions the most, the paper aims to study the complex ways in which vulnerability to climate change is affected by caste and social relations. The paper draws on a statistical analysis of the data on victims of extreme weather events to ascertain intersectionality. In addition, a textual analysis of the frameworks/policies and governance mechanisms will be undertaken to understand how caste is represented to reveal the different forms of social, cultural, political capital and technological know-how that enable the most marginalised castes to cope with disasters. This paper aims to contribute towards caste-sensitive capacity building programmes for coping with climate change impacts.

Global Patriarchies and Transnational Women and Feminists for Climate Justice *Julie Maria Gorecki, UC Berkeley*

Scholars and international organizations have shown that climate change disproportionately affects women across the globe. Indigenous women and women in the Global South are especially impacted. In response Women and Feminists for Climate Justice are mobilizing transnationally and with unified demands towards a "feminist system change, not climate change" (Gorecki 2015). Drawing on five years of extensive multi-sited ethnographies and

interviews, this paper maps and compares the narratives and experiences of Women and Feminists for Climate Justice activists from around the world. It asks, how do women and gender non-binary people across six continents invoke “good relations” of collectivity between them to enact shared rhetoric, advocacy, and international solidarities regarding climate and gender? In what similar and different ways does climate change burden them, and what do their responses to these questions reveal about the nexus between climate change and gender on a global structural level? This paper is also grounded in theoretical questions regarding the relationship between Racial Capitalism, Patriarchy and the Environment (Robinson 1983; Pulido 2016). Many transnational and ecological feminists have affirmed that capitalism’s founding ideology of continuous growth has been necessitated by the coincident subordination of women, racialized and marginalized communities, and nature. They reference this interdependent subordination as the “Capitalist Patriarchy” (often reinterpreted as the “imperialist white supremacist cis-heterosexual capitalist patriarchy” within the movement) — a global “anti-woman” system founded on the exploitation of women’s power, bodies, labor and epistemologies through violent histories of colonialism and white supremacy. (Mies 1984; Gorecki 2020).

Water-Thinks: Anti Colonialism from the Margins of Empire

Ela Przybylo, Illinois State University

Black Diaspora Studies’ and African American Studies’ water theory (i.e., Amideo 2021; Brathwaite 1999; Gilroy 1993; Glissant 1989; Gumbs 2018; Lethabo King 2019; Spillers 1987; Tinsley 2008), has challenged material, political, and affective understandings of water. For example, metaphors of water and ocean have been developed to think about the violence and trauma of the Atlantic trade of human bodies and to challenge Western colonial genealogies of thought. In this piece, I will draw on Black water analytics to theorize both moves to freedom and “moves to innocence” as they relate to the tangled histories of the Central and Eastern European (CEE) nation-state of Poland (Tuck and Yang 2012). I use water analytics to theorize, first, Poland’s ongoing movements to freedom such as the literal escape of thousands from state-socialism to Nordic democratic countries throughout the years of Soviet rule, with attempts made in underwater vessels, through swimming, and through jumping off of cruise ships into Nordic waters. Yet I argue that water analytics also require questioning “innocence” to examine colonial attachments to conquest – or as Lethabo King names them, fantasies of “conquistador-humanism” invested in the superiority of whiteness (Lethabo King 2019). This piece aims to contribute to broader conversations around water analytics with an attention to the movement of queer, colonial, and anti-colonial knowledge-production. It reflects on possibilities for placing marginalized European nations, such as Poland, in dialogue with the foundational work of Black and Indigenous studies and for drawing up strategies of accounting for colonial violence in the context of nations themselves oppressed. It contributes specifically to STS by centralizing Black feminist ecocriticism, and to a smaller extent Indigenous ecocriticism, alongside CEE transnational studies.

Mercurial Landscapes and Global Epistemic Infrastructures:

Capacity-Building, Patrimonialization, and the Uneven Geographies of Mercury Toxicity *Sebastian Rubiano-Galvis, University of California, Berkeley*

The call to “Make Mercury History,” as the 2013 UN Minamata Convention on Mercury motto states, reveals tensions between the legacies of an indestructible, persistent substance and the hopes for a detoxified future without it. Such tensions are tangible in the realm of mercury reduction initiatives in the artisanal and small-scale gold mining sector (ASGM), which build on a long history of knowledge production, technology transfer, and capacity-building projects in countries like Colombia and Peru. Through a multi-site ethnography,

interviews, and document analysis, my research dissects the emergence and unfolding of the anti-mercury global regime spearheaded by UN and aid agencies, philanthropists, and states in the past forty years. In particular, I focus on the attempts to know and build the ASGM sector’s capacity through specific technologies and epistemic practices and how miners engage (or not) with them. Drawing on STS, discard studies, disability studies, and global environmental politics concepts, my paper examines how the politics of expertise and knowledge about global mercury pollution shapes conversations over which mercurial landscapes are worth knowing, intervening, patrimonializing, or left to degrade. Drawing on the Minamata Convention unfolding in Colombia (through capacity-building and knowledge transfer projects) and the 2012 UNESCO declaration of the Almadén mercury mines in Spain as a cultural heritage site, I interrogate the uneven register of the “capacities” and materiality of mercurial landscapes under these global epistemic infrastructures and reflect upon how the emerging geographies of toxicity risk neglecting toxic colonial legacies and accentuating current toxic injustices in ASGM.

Session Organizer:

William San Martin, Worcester Polytechnic Institute (WPI)

Chair:

William San Martin, Worcester Polytechnic Institute (WPI)

Discussant:

William San Martin, Worcester Polytechnic Institute (WPI)

485. AI and Feminist STS - II

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Much excellent work has documented how contemporary artificial intelligence (AI) systems reinforce and deepen historical inequalities and oppressions. Further work remains, however, on whether and how AI systems can do otherwise. Recent social movements within AI research have begun to politicize AI technologies and their entanglements with social justice, power relations, and environmentalism (see, for example, #TechWontBuildIt and recent ACM special issues on “AI Activism” and “Green AI”). In a current technology ecosystem dominated by commercial and military interests, however, few possibilities seem to exist for AI practitioners to “strive towards good relations” among humans, technologies, and environments. This panel seeks to investigate how theories, methods, and ways of knowing from decades of feminist STS scholarship can inform the study of AI systems as they are used today. In Alison Adam’s (1995) feminist critique of AI epistemology, she emphasizes the need for more concrete examples of a “successor science” based on feminist epistemology and social constructivism to ground AI research. What would “successor AI” look like, built on feminist principles of situated knowledges and standpoint theory? Beyond universalized, depoliticized notions of “ethical AI,” might an analysis using feminist STS ground AI systems in complex sociotechnical entanglements and particular histories, geographies, communities, and contexts? This panel features work that engages with these questions and imagines new possibilities for feminist AI technologies. Topics include, but are not limited to, the following: * Social and political movements that aim to centre ethics of care, entanglement, relationality, and responsibility in human-AI systems * Indigenous, Black, feminist, and queer conceptualizations of “artificial intelligence” * Disability studies, feminist STS, and artificial intelligence * Ecofeminism, environmental justice, “green AI” and environmental impacts of AI systems * Standpoint theory and the politics of image, speech, and emotion recognition systems * Intersections and contradictions between feminist health projects and AI in healthcare * New methods and imagined futures for feminist, de-/anti-colonial, anti-military, anti-carceral, anti-capitalist AI Keywords: feminist STS, artificial intelligence, technofeminism, feminist technologies, ethical AI

Participants:

Big data and fertility: Identifying areas of concern in the development and use of fertility tracking technologies *Alina Geampana, Aston University*

The Femtech industry has grown massively in recent years, with a projected US\$50 billion valuation by 2025 (Kressbach, 2019). Fertility tracking technologies (FTTs) constitute one of the largest segments of this market. These either take the form of digital applications (commonly referred to as ‘apps’) where users input relevant data or wearable monitoring devices. FTTs give users algorithmic predictions about their fertile windows. Millions of women use such technologies to track their fertility and manage their reproductive health. Technology companies now use refined algorithms that generate an unprecedented amount of data about user fertility patterns and associated health conditions. However, the sector remains largely unregulated and we have little knowledge on how fertility algorithms are developed, how the data collected are used by companies, accessed by researchers and provided by users (Epstein et al., 2017; Gambier-Ross et al., 2018; Lupton, 2018). Informed by an analysis of key documents and secondary sources, this paper argues that there are several systemic areas of concern that contribute to inequalities in the use of FTTs. These include: 1) the development of app algorithms and advanced FTT AI; 2) the development of data infrastructures; 3) surveillance practices; 4) the quality of the user experience; and 5) a lack of attention to potential uses in clinical practice. In its conclusion, the paper explores potential pathways towards maximizing beneficial uses of FTTs and the vast amount of data that they generate.

Disability Expertise in Making AI Work *Di Wu, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)*

People with disabilities are typically imagined as victims, beneficiaries, or inspirations of AI. This paper examines an under-discussed role that disabled people play in AI systems – labor. I focus on a China-based team of disabled data workers who sort, label, and categorize training data for voice-activated AI (VAI) systems. Based on remote interviews and preliminary pre-pandemic fieldwork, I show how these blind, low-vision, or physically impaired workers, through centering the ethics of care, access, and interdependence, reshape work in AI production. I argue that AI developers in China profit from systemic ableism and disability expertise, not the other way around. The inherent ambiguity of human intention categorization that current VAI systems rely on, mobilizes a stable, trained workforce of data taggers, which disabled people in the absence of better structural opportunities end up fulfilling. Yet not all “disability + tagging” programs succeed. In this study, a disability NGO organized the workers to negotiate and improve the working conditions of data annotation. Specifically, they deploy situated knowledge of “crip time” management, and the co-creation of access. These forms of “disability expertise,” grounded in the heterogenous lived experience of disability, I argue, are key to improving the work performance and work experience of AI data processing. Building upon scholarship of feminist STS and crip technoscience, this paper calls for attention to the knowledge and expertise of disabled people in human-AI systems. Centering the co-creation of enabling conditions rather than essentialized body-minds, disability expertise offers a new methodology for imagining counterhegemonic AI.

Menstruation Defined By Design: How Menstrual Tracking Apps Influence Our Understanding Of The Menstrual Cycle *Kathleen McCormick, Cornell University; Jane Mendle, Advisor, co-author*

In the past decade, life data tracking has increased and the market for collecting health and behavioral data has produced a variety of options with data collected and saved on the application that is often offered for free or for a low cost. In particular, an increasing number of apps have been created to track menstrual cycles. As companies begin to monetize menstrual cycle tracking through digital applications, it is important to examine the interface that the users will encounter and how the meaning of menstruation is co-constructed by both the app design and the user. In particular it is important to consider how the use of these

apps shape our individual and collective knowledge of menstruation. The present study examined three menstrual cycle tracking apps using The Walkthrough Method to examine three popular menstrual tracking apps. In utilizing The Walkthrough Method, several themes were identified throughout all of the apps: health marketing, implied demographics, and nudges towards reproduction. The interface of all three menstrual tracking apps suggest that technologies are mirroring back user’s own menstrual cycle data in a science-backed analysis, when apps are, in fact, mirroring back gendered assumptions about menstruation and mood consistent with cultural narratives through the user interface. I argue that these assumptions enact harm through an exclusive design for able-bodied, young, heterosexual, and cisgender women, with the symbolic annihilation of those who do not possess the culturally defined “average” menstrual cycle due to age, health, sexual identity, or sexual orientation.

Reworking AI: Using Ethnography and Design Inquiry to Illuminate the Sociotechnical Work of Automation *Samantha Shorey, University of Texas; Sarah Fox, Carnegie Mellon University*

Recognition of the constitutive and often unseen labor that underpins technological systems is central to the project of feminist science and technology studies scholarship. Through the lens of “invisible labor,” feminist STS scholars illuminate how workplace activities or workers themselves may be hidden through obscurity or abstraction (Star & Strauss, 1999). This invisibility limits the ability of workers to guide the process of technology development, even as they’re tasked with handling the problems that arise because of it. More than merely artifacts, Artificially Intelligent (AI) technologies are sustained by a sociotechnical system of human-machine relations (Suchman, 2007). Practices such as calibration, troubleshooting, maintenance and repair are performed by those who work alongside automated technologies. In the proposed paper, we explore how methods grounded in feminist STS scholarship may be used to not only show the presence of the invisible work that sustains AI, but promote workers as valued contributors to design processes. Using methods of ethnography and design inquiry, our project investigates how workers adopt and adapt AI technologies throughout their implementation. In particular, we focus on AI deployed in two waste labor industries—airport sanitation and recycling sorting—in response to the Covid-19 pandemic. We reflect on how field observation and participatory workshops with workers bring to light overlooked problems (and possible alternatives) for the pursuit of ‘good relations’ between humans and AI. In doing so, we challenge design narratives that position engineer’s intentions as the source of “ethical AI” and that position worker’s experiences in the realm of unanticipated consequences. We offer a feminist, worker-centered approach to design research as a vantage point for recognizing AI outcomes as a political project.

Situated Bots: positioning non-humans within behavioral counselling and care-giving. *Matt Ratto, University of Toronto; Camille Intson, University of Toronto; Olivia Doggett, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto; Mathew Iantorno, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto*

Therapeutic AI-powered conversational bots have been described as ‘non-positional’ - having no specific body or human experience to draw upon, they are therefore seen as not having any specific ‘position’ to take that might reduce their capacity to provide unbiased guidance or support for individuals seeking help. Their non-judgmental nature is understood as having an important benefit in contexts where social stigma might reduce the possibility of people seeking assistance. This paper examines the idea of ‘non-positionality’ of bots, noting its relation to similar technological neutrality arguments of the past. We describe the

downsides of believing bots to be 'non-positional' while also recognizing the potential therapeutic benefits as noted by others. We propose that bots, rather than being non-positional, in fact inhabit a position that is specific to their own status as non-human entities, produced by humans, and intended to mirror in some ways human interactions. Using the pilot study of a therapeutic bot project in which we are participants, we explore the particular ways in which this bot is being constructed to take on a specific form of non-human positionality which, among other things, is designed to effect a sense of its own non-human nature. We leverage ideas of situated knowledge drawn from feminist science studies to highlight the ways in which non-positionality is performed and the positive and negative ramifications of these design choices.

Towards a Performative Conceptualization of Artificial Intelligence *Eleanor DRAGE, The University of Cambridge; Federica Frabetti, University of Roehampton*

This paper explores how theories of performativity can make visible how AI enacts and produces the gendered and racialised reality it is imagined to observe. To examine how AI produces, performs, and polices systems of race and gender we draw on Karen Barad's posthumanist performativity, Nadine Ehler's work on race and performativity and Judith Butler's contention that gender does not pre-exist a person: gender emerges through a subject's interaction with and 'citation' of the power structures that sediment gender norms. We argue that, by using unprecedented sums of data to achieve an objective, AI is especially performative in its ability to sustain and enforce racist and sexist norms. We take as an example of this the higher classification error rates for dark-skinned and asian women than for white men in current face recognition technologies. The systematic production of a field of intelligibility which excludes certain bodies determines which subjects come 'to matter' in society and which are marginalized. We explore the modes of resistance to normative paradigms opened up by a performative understanding of AI, from practices of disidentification that draw attention to the incalculability of a face to a feminist AI framework that makes visible and accounts for the excluded pathways and obfuscations necessary for face recognition systems to produce actionable outputs. Ultimately, we suggest that a feminist and queer framework for AI would acknowledge that AI technologies are always grounded in a specific time, place, and context and must be studied in their singularity, rather than according to a disembodied and formalized model of AI ethics.

Session Organizer:

Rachel Bergmann, Microsoft Research New England

486. Rethinking Sexuality Amid Pharmacological Sex Therapies I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Participants:

An Exploration of Perceptions of and/or Experiences Using Poppers Among MSM *Jennifer Katz, Brown School of Public Health; Jacob van den Berg, Brown School of Public Health; Katie Biello, Brown School of Public Health*
Poppers (alkyl nitrite inhalants) are recreational substances commonly used during sexual activity by gay, bisexual, or other men who have sex with men (MSM). The obscure legal status of poppers in the U.S. has permitted their sustained accessibility in adult bookstores while forbidding any discussion of their use as an inhalant. Few qualitative studies have analyzed the sociocultural perceptions and experiential patterns of popper-use among MSM. Poppers occupy many intertwining narratives: a material transformation from a medication, a legacy in gay dance scenes, an anomaly in drug legislation, and a significant role in the sexual lives of MSM. This qualitative study investigates perceptions of and/or experiences with popper-use among MSM

through in-depth interviews with twenty MSM in the U.S. who have used, currently use, or are familiar with poppers. Using grounded theory analysis, the following four themes were identified in the interviews: (1) utility, (2) cultural community, (3) stigma, and (4) information-seeking. These themes underscore the extent to which the ability to confidently make informed decisions around popper-use is undermined by the silence around poppers. Though there are health risks associated with popper-use that must be addressed, the multidimensional experience that many MSM recount in their use of poppers particularly as a tool during sex as well as an artifact that connects them to the broader queer community must also be recognized. Greater publicly accessible resources and more discussion around poppers, centered on pleasure and harm-reduction, are needed to limit their harmful effects without further stigmatizing MSM.

Desire Pills, Love Sprays, Maternity Drops: Pharmacological Normativity and the Reproduction of the "Ideal" Conjuality *Arbel Griner, Princeton University; Rafaela Teixeira Zorzanelli, State University of Rio de Janeiro*

Our paper presents and explores the participation of available and commercialized pharmacology in the forging of the neurochemical "love complex" – a composite of neurohormones and neuropeptides that, according to neuroscientific literature, interact to guarantee human reproduction and survival. Such theory connects lust, infatuation and long-lasting affective bonds in humans to neural correlates in the brain, and has been used by prominent Anglo-Saxon bioethicists to conjecture about ethical frameworks for the pharmacological neuroenhancement of heteronormative relationships centered around childrearing. Following and analyzing such hypothesis and its appropriation by contemporary bioethics, we want to reflect on the construction of the love complex as a scientific fact, and scrutinize the modes in which pharmaceutical molecules and their broad network of official and unofficial prescribers and consumers co-produce such fact. As we illuminate the hormonal assemblages, neurobiological circuitry, scientific power/knowledges, practices and values that coalesce around the material-semiotics of a love complex, we will also reveal the intimate interlocution between pharmaceutical products and scientific design, experimentation and normative findings. Evolutionary and neurochemical at the same time, the love complex has become a nexus that brings together biopolitical mechanisms that aim to instruct towards the reproduction of specific affective norms. This epistemic entity hails and entails concrete effects spanning from pharmacological aids in couple therapy; new diagnostic categories; chemically-based treatment protocols and enhancement practices; and scientific theories and experiments that reiterate preferred (or "normal") affective arrangements – heterosexual, long-lasting, child-centered, and biologically and economically productive.

Performativity of HIV Science and Biomedical Technologies in Queer Men's Sexual Practices *Emerich Daroya, Dalla Lana School of Public Health, University of Toronto*

In this paper, I focus on the performativity of HIV science and technologies to attend to its implication in men who have sex with men's (MSM) sexual practices. This paper asks: what role does HIV scientific and medical knowledge play in queer men's embodied practices of biomedical technologies; and how does the consumption of HIV pharmaceuticals alter sexual practices and subjectivities. Analysing data gathered from an online forum and interviews with users of Pre-Exposure Prophylaxis (PrEP), I suggest that MSM integrate biomedical technologies and HIV medicine into embodied practices to make sense of the effectiveness and safety of antiretroviral drugs (ARVs). Likewise, the embodiment of HIV knowledge informs understandings of uncertainties and limitations by emphasising that biomedical technologies do not wholly provide zero risks. However, rather than constraining sexual practices, doubts about

ARVs allow users to invent different harm reduction strategies, offering MSM to re-examine fears around HIV, open spaces for agency and empowerment, and enable men to achieve pleasure. Thus, while public health maintains the presumption that MSM are responsible for sexual behavioural changes due to HIV pharmaceutical technologies, the performative approach I propose in this paper recasts HIV science and medicine as active participants in shaping sexual practices. This paper responds to Kane Race's (2016) call to attend to science's active role in shaping sexualities and forms of pleasure.

Session Organizer:

Amaya Perez-Brumer, University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health

Chair:

Amaya Perez-Brumer, University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health

Discussant:

César Torres Cruz, Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios de Género (CIEG). Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

487. Transparency and Algorithmic Governance - II: Theorizing and approaching transparency and algorithmic governance

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Participants:

Transparent Dreams (Are Made of This): Counterfactuals as Transparency Tools in Automated Decision Making *Katja De Vries*

This paper gives a legal-conceptual analysis of the use of counterfactuals (what-if explanations) as transparency tools for automated decision making (ADM). The first part of the analysis discusses three notions: transparency, ADM and generative artificial intelligence (AI). The second part of this article takes a closer look at the pros and cons of counterfactuals in making ADM explainable. Transparency is only useful if it is actionable, that is, if it challenges systemic bias or unjustified decisions. Existing ways of providing transparency about ADM systems are often limited in terms of being actionable. In contrast to many existing transparency tools, counterfactual explanations hold the promise of providing actionable and individually tailored transparency while not revealing too much of the model (attractive if ADM is a trade secret or if it is important that the system cannot be gamed). Another strength of counterfactuals is that they show that transparency should not be understood as the immediate visibility of some underlying truth. While promising, counterfactuals have their limitations. Firstly, there is always a multiplicity of counterfactuals (the Rashomon effect). Secondly, counterfactual explanations are not natural givens. Instead, they are constructed and the many underlying design decisions can turn out for better or worse.

Transparency Multiple: Algorithmic Regulation And The Governance Of Terrorist And Extremist Content (TVEC) Online *Dimitri Van Den Meerssche*, *Edinburgh Law School, University of Edinburgh*; *Gavin Sullivan*, *Edinburgh Law School, University of Edinburgh*

'Transparency' has become a central reference point and mediating device in the political controversies surrounding platform governance of terrorist and violent extremist content (TVEC) online. It is a key part of platform self-regulation efforts, best-practice standards of international organisations, commitments of informal industry-led fora and multi-stakeholder initiatives, and diverse regulatory initiatives currently under discussion in states and regional organisations. This paper sheds light on the different political demands, conceptual underpinnings, governance practices and rationalities of rule at play in these varying and conflicting invocations of the principle. It empirically investigates the work transparency is doing in key

regulatory sites of TVEC governance – including in the UK Online Harms Framework, the EU Digital Services Act (and proposed EU Regulation on Preventing the Dissemination of Terrorist Content Online), the Global Internet Forum to Counter Terrorism (GIFCT) and the OECD's emerging 'voluntary transparency reporting framework. Employing ANT's material-semiotic method, our paper maps the terrain of 'transparency multiple' (Cf. Mol 2002) as one where different political projects and computational ontologies are negotiated and enacted. We show how the governance technology of 'transparency reporting' is fast becoming the global standard through which broader conflicts around platform power are channelled and framed, and ask what is at stake in this process – following what this transparency reporting governance move authorises, smooths over and forecloses in debates on the platform governance of TVEC online.

The archival opacity of social media platforms' policies *Joao Carlos Magalhães*

The rules established by social media platforms to govern the behaviour of their billions of users are among the most important private policies in the world. Yet, not much has been written on how these policies changed over time, an aspect that seems essential to understand the transformation of these platforms into dominant spaces of global communication. Focussing on Facebook, YouTube, Twitter, Instagram and Sound Cloud, this paper debates some methodological difficulties involved in the historical research of these rules, and presents the blueprint of an open repository of platforms' policies. Its first part argues that platforms' policies appear to be concealed by what we term archival opacity. By that we mean that these policies are hidden from view by the way they are and are not archived in the platforms' websites. Current policies are not restricted to those of documents such as terms of service and privacy agreements. In fact, over time, they have become fragmented into sometimes dozens of URLs, buried in various Help pages that are not easily found by ordinary users. Previous policies are even harder to find. Few platforms have clearly organised archives, and existent archives are either incomplete (e.g. Twitter) or confusingly designed (e.g. Facebook). The paper provides evidence of these inconsistencies and entertain some hypotheses that can explain them. The second part of the paper proposes that this sort of archival opacity calls for a public, transparent and independently built online repository, which we are currently developing -- the 'Platform Governance Archive'.

#FuckTheAlgorithm: algorithmic imaginaries and political resistance *Garfield Benjamin*, *Solent University*

The A-Level results algorithm debacle in the UK generated a major act of collective resistance by students against biased systems of power. But this resistance was not about bias in the dataset or flaws in technical implementation. It was about resisting algorithms working as intended, resisting the purposeful perpetuation of inequities in which futures are determined by historical data as representative of historical social bias. This paper will build on the A-Level example and others - such as doctors resisting algorithmic vaccine allocation - to explore political resistance in and of algorithmic imaginaries. Building on the work of Taina Bucher and Becky Kazansky/Stefania Milan, everyday algorithmic imaginaries will intersect with algorithmic resistance. The everyday will be traced back through the #FuckTheAlgorithm hashtag, from individual mundane exclamations of frustration through to its rallying cry in the 2020 student protests and on to a symbol of resistance to algorithmic decision-making. Futures of resistance and decision-making will be discussed alongside present day resistance to the intrusion of algorithms on the everyday. The asymmetric visibility and experience of these imaginaries will be discussed, to examine the symbolic points of mass resistance against the constant marginalisation of certain groups within their own everyday experience of algorithms. The paper will outline everyday

imaginaries of resistance in which the appropriation of algorithmic reductionism - the abstraction of humans into data reclaimed in the abstraction of structural bias into a hashtag - and how these imaginaries are establishing ways of speaking across the everyday and the exceptional towards greater algorithmic justice.

A view from everywhere? Multidisciplinary collaboration in studies of algorithmic transparency *Jaakko Taipale, University of Helsinki; Ida Koivisto, University of Helsinki; Riikka Koulu, University of Helsinki*

The calls for algorithmic transparency involve a number of interpretations of the very idea of transparency. These interpretations stem from contextual inquiries of AI and its societal applications and consequences, and, depending on the disciplinary perspective, different facets of algorithmic transparency become visible: legal, conceptual, socio-material, technological, and cultural. Should we settle for this fragmented view? Indeed, what are the dis-/advantages of such fragmentation? If we opt for learning through interdisciplinary dialogue, should we also push for unified and constructive arrangements of joint knowledge production on the shared research interest? How would this be best organized, and what are the expected positive and negative consequences and experiences to be expected? These are the main learning objectives of the discussion that we would like to host at the panel. To frame the discussion, we reflect on the work of a recently formed research group that shares a common research interest in algorithmic transparency. The group combines legal doctrinal, sociolegal and STS approaches to the topic and its empirical and conceptual examination. Initial observations point to disciplinary tendencies to fasten attention into differing points of interest and to a diverging empirical agenda, despite efforts to the contrary. Drawing from earlier STS work on multidisciplinary collaboration, our presentation explores the potential and challenges of collaboration between legal and sociological (STS) scholars especially, and its potential in examining the joint topic of algorithmic transparency

Session Organizer:

Jaakko Taipale, University of Helsinki

Chair:

Suvi Sankari, University of Helsinki, Finland

488. Wiring digital justice: Embedding rights in Internet governance by infrastructure - I

9:40 to 11:10 am

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Session subtitle: "Infrastructures as Interfaces of Activism, Resistance and Control" This session seeks to explore how the language of civil rights and freedoms can be translated in the language and materiality of infrastructures and what the complexities are that arise from this process. As Keller Easterling (2014) writes "changes to the globalizing world are being written, not in the language of law and diplomacy, but rather in the language of infrastructure". From Internet routing protocols to network architecture solutions, infrastructures "set the invisible rules that govern the spaces of our everyday lives" (Ibid). From Iran to Germany, this session brings up a selection of ethnographic research exploring how different forms of grassroots, local and activist-led tech activism are encoding freedoms into tools, protocols and everyday practices.

Participants:

Assembling digital infrastructures in alternative housing & activism *Andrea Schikowitz, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies*

While social movements and activists are well aware of the politics and performativity of digital tools and platforms, they rely on these technologies for promoting and realising their goals and projects (Ilten & McInerney, 2020). Thus, using digital technologies in reflexive ways and finding ways of navigating

dilemmas between utility, data politics and precaution is crucial for social movements (Corsin Jiménez, 2014). In this paper, I focus on activist collaborative housing groups in Vienna (Mullins & Moore, 2018), who aim at contributing to decommodification of housing and to alternative ways of living in community. I empirically analyse how they assemble their digital infrastructures (Bowker, Baker, Millerand, & Ribes, 2010) for facilitating collaboration, knowledge management and communication. Thereby, they use commercial tools and platforms in specific ways, draw on open source software and produce and self-host digital tools. I pay attention to their infrastructuring process – i.e. how they evaluate and negotiate the use of specific tools, how they try to avoid specific (mis-)uses of the data, and how they combine different tools as well as how they relate digital and other knowledge practices. The empirical materials stem from a multi-sited ethnography of different collaborative housing projects in Vienna. I conducted interviews, observations of public and semi-public events and analysed social media appearances.

Carving Out Tunnels: Re-creating Communications and Circumventing Censorship in Iran *Raha Peyravi, Massachusetts Institute for Technology (MIT)*

Iran as a country is no stranger to internet censorship. In November 2019 however, the country faced an unexpected episode: an almost complete internet shutdown, making all commonly used tools for circumventing censorship useless. This caused a new wave for explorations in ways to leverage the existing communication infrastructure and find ways to circumvent censorship. Except, the groups at the forefront of these creative ventures were not only activists and network engineers but groups of cryptocurrency miners and traders who by the nature of their sometimes legally hazy work rely on stable, uninterrupted, and surveillance resistant connections. This is both to secure their profit and avoid the risk of finding themselves vulnerable to government's raid on illegal mining operations. . In this project, I follow the conversations of online communities of cryptocurrency miners and traders who have developed a certain level of "experiential expertise" through the day to day work of maintaining their mining operations, troubleshooting connections to mining pools, bitcoin wallets and exchange platforms. While not experts in network engineering, these communities continuously tinker with protocols, ports, and routers in ways inaccessible to an average user or even an average crypto miner. I show how "trust" figures as an important concern in conversations where users challenge each other's expertise, and describe how they navigate uncertainties around "credible knowledge". At the same time, I argue that the work of these groups, while primarily aimed at securing their own profit, can be considered a form of "auxiliary activism" (Easterling, 2014). In other words, taking seriously the informal and experiential forms of knowledge could potentially help imagine resilient and sustainable communication infrastructures.

Conceptualizing "Sociotechnical Interventions" in Digital Infrastructures: Case studies of "tech activism" *Stephane Couture, Université de Montréal*

We propose to reflect on the concept of "sociotechnical interventions" to apprehend diverse forms of activism and engagement aiming at creating or transforming technological infrastructures. While the concept of "sociotechnical interventions" does not seem to have been explicitly conceptualized in STS, many authors have used similar terms. Feenberg (2004), in his critical theory of technology, uses the term "democratic rationalization" to refer to interventions that aim to defy non-democratic power relationships inscribed in modern technologies. Hess (2005) uses the term "Technology- and product-oriented movements (TPMs)" to emphasize "mobilizations of civil society organizations [...] for which the target of social change is support for an alternative technology [...]" (p. 515). Suchman (2007) argues that a form of intervention

in technological practices consists at looking at how humans and machines are figured in these practices, and how they can be reconfigured otherwise (p. 227). Our presentation will both reflect on the use of similar concepts in existing literature and on observations in our current research on technological proposals made by social movements in the context of Internet Governance. In particular, we propose to look at “sociotechnical interventions” through different case studies we have conducted in the last few years around these three axes: 1) The engagement of civil society actors in the development of Internet standards and protocols; 2) The propositions of alternative digital platforms or services, in particular by and for feminist groups; and 3) The development of community networks. We will analyze discourses, practices, and imaginaries involved in these interventions.

Encoding Freedom: Analysis of open search technology between German hacker ethics and Asian start-up culture
Astrid Mager, Austrian Academy of Sciences

SUSI.AI is an open source personal assistant that has its roots in decentralized technology, peer-to-peer principles and the German hacker culture. It is devoted to values and rights of the Free Software movement: „access to source code is a fundamental right“ (Stallman, cited in Birkinbine 2020). With the recent move of SUSI.AI towards Asia, however, other cultural visions, values and notions of freedom entered the developer community. SUSI.AI is still relying on the initial hacker community, but also making use of the Google summer of code program funding open source project, for example. This indicates that free software is not entirely independent from corporate players, quite on the contrary (Birkinbine 2020, Coleman 2013). In a sense, both hands are feeding each other, but one of them is much more powerful than the other. Drawing on concepts from STS such as “vanguard visions” (Hilgartner 2015), values by design (Von Hippel 2006), and the political economy of free software (Birkinbine (2020) this presentation will pose the following questions: What visions, values and rights are driving SUSI.AI and how are they encoded in the technology? What compromises are SUSI developers willing to make to remain capable to act? And how do they handle the balancing act between free software and corporate actors? And, on a more general level, what are the wider sociopolitical implications in terms of tech development; especially in Europe where fundamental rights are framed as “core European values” (Mager 2017)? These questions will be answered based on a rich body of qualitative research materials including interviews with German, Asian and US-American SUSI.AI/ open source developers, participatory observations of open tech events in Frankfurt (CCC), Berlin and Singapore (FOSSASIA) and two joint workshops with SUSI.AI developers. This research is funded by the Austrian Science Fund (FWF, project number: V511-G29).

Session Organizer:

Ksenia Ermoshina, CNRS

Chair:

Stefania Milan, University of Amsterdam, The Netherlands

489. Interrogating "co-creation": the good, the bad, and the ugly - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

Initiatives to stimulate innovation through “co-creation” among diverse actors are proliferating, whether driven from the top-down through governments and policy instruments (e.g. in living labs, public procurement of innovation and pre-commercial procurement) or bottom-up by business or civil society (e.g. in social innovation). But can and does co-creation (in its multiple configurations) really contribute to democratizing innovation, legitimizing interventions, addressing grand societal challenges, and facilitating sociotechnical transitions? How is co-creation enacted in practice? How do power asymmetries and incumbency shape co-creation

outcomes? What are the possibilities and problems of efforts to scale-up co-creation across different locations? And how should we interrogate the practices, rhetoric, and normative implications of co-creation? In this panel, we interrogate the processes, practices, problems, publics and power structures surrounding the inflationary use of “co-creation” as remedy for innovation skepticism and democratic deficits — often combined with effort of up-scaling and replication its processes and results. We welcome empirical cases drawing on a variety of methods, analyses of co-creative practices that build on extant concepts in STS and neighboring fields, and new theoretical and conceptual developments. Comparative approaches across national boundaries, co-creation instruments, and technological domains and applications are more than welcome. Session 2 includes papers that discuss the different ways in which citizens are involved in co-creation initiatives.

Participants:

Co-creation in (citizen) science: Unbundling the concept and identifying key challenges
Julia Suess-Reyes, Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft; Susanne Beck, LBG OIS Center & Copenhagen Business School; Robin Brehm, Ludwig Boltzmann Gesellschaft; Marion Poetz, Copenhagen Business School; Henry Sauermann, ESMT Berlin

Co-creating together with citizens is increasingly gaining importance in a variety of contexts. A particularly interesting context is academic science, which often serves as source for innovation, due to the large knowledge distance between citizens and professional scientists. In an attempt to democratize science, we observe a trend moving from contributory citizen science projects with rather low-complex labor inputs towards more co-creative approaches that grant citizens enhanced decision rights and promise to generate meaning for all parties. However, while much has been written about co-creation (e.g., in innovation, customer involvement and design co-creation), the foundations of the concept in a science context remain fuzzy and its realized potential unclear. We address this gap conceptually by refining the definition of co-creation in science and empirically by providing insights on key challenges of co-created citizen science projects. We collect data from ten co-created citizen science projects varying along different dimensions (e.g., the type of citizens’ contributions, the research process steps with citizen involvement, their level of shared decision rights, and regarding exogenous criteria such as the research field). Through an inductive-deductive iterative coding process, we analyze 23 interviews with project coordinators and citizen scientists and comprehensive secondary data. We identify key challenges particular to co-creation in science as well as related contingencies. Our findings contribute to research on the organization of science and distributed knowledge production. Our insights can inform professional scientists and citizens who want to collaborate as well as policymakers and funders as part of designing grant requirements.

Co-creating an Innovative and Technological Society: Looking for the Co-creating Citizen in the “Smart” Paris Region
Carole-Anne Tisserand, ECOLE DES MINES DE PARIS

This paper focuses on co-creation processes in the context of a “smart” territory project. It is based on a participant observation in the Paris Region carried out in the context of my doctoral research, and analyzes a program called “Construire au Futur, Habiter le Futur” (Building the Future, Inhabiting the Future) which targets the digital, housing and construction sectors. This program involves local authorities and private companies in order to facilitate the development of public interest technologies. It comprises an explicit ambition of citizen participation addressed to citizens, local administrative bodies and companies, and framed in the language of co-creation. I analyze the co-creation methods used by the Paris Region as technologies of participation which aims to perform public and public engagement (Barry, 2001; Felt and Fochler, 2010; Irwin, 2001; Laurent, 2011; Rose, 1999; Voß, Amelung, 2016). Raising

the question of which political subject is produced by the innovation processes pushing companies, public authorities and citizens to co-create, I discuss the constant search for a “co-creating subject” and the difficulties it faces. I first describe the disappearance of the “citizen” in favor of the “user”. Then I show that the imperative to co-create is in fact an unshared conviction: co-creation is seen more as a means to create new business relationships and market opportunities. Citizens are excluded from the process. Thus the co-creating citizen is seen as an elusive figure, useful to be part of the national agenda but difficult to bring into existence.

Enacting “mine” and “our”: how stakeholder experiences of ownership impact co-creation *Shelly Tsui, Eindhoven University of Technology*

Extant research has identified the role of motivation, needs, and interests to explain what drives consumers, companies, organizations, and society to co-create. However, it has not been examined how stakeholders stay active and engaged during co-creation. In addition to significant investment of capital, time, resources, energy, more importantly, co-creation also requires its stakeholders to possess, or to eventually develop skills and capabilities, that enables the active engagement with other stakeholders and the process itself. The matter of skills and capabilities, or even the need to develop them, has not been conceptually or empirically researched and renders the “active” engagement in co-creation rather unclear. To address this, we apply the theory of psychological ownership from organizational studies to shed light on how individuals enact active participation i.e. respond and exert their agency, in multi-stakeholder settings. Psychological ownership is described as identifying a target as “this is mine”, and that this possession-based feeling (attitude) towards their target/environment influences their actions (behavior). We conducted semi-structured interviews with subjects from a Dutch case study on sustainable housing, CASA, on their experience on how they engaged with the project. Through examining the subjects’ experiences, we identified attitudes and behaviors, attributed as skills and capabilities, that enabled their active engagement, as well as the barriers. We conclude with two insights: one, stakeholder ownership experiences offer a window to the complex and simultaneous processes that constitute active engagement in co-creation. Two, experiences situate the skills and capabilities present and those desired. This reinforces the needed sensitivity towards the local context when deciding on what abilities to foster.

Engaging the indifferent and the indignant *Thomas Berker, Department Of Interdisciplinary Studies Of Culture, Norwegian University Of Science And Technology,*

Citizens that do not care about the issue at stake in a co-creation and co-design process (the indifferent) and those who are not willing to engage with different perspectives (the indignant) are systematically excluded from participation. This is particularly problematic if an issue potentially affects all citizens and at the same time produces indifference and indignation. Climate change is such an issue: for the indifferent it is a kind of ‘background noise’ (Norgaard 2011) which is drowned by other concerns. And a growing group of indignants sees calls for action against climate change as yet another way to subject ‘the little man’ to rules and restrictions serving ‘cosmopolitan elites’ (Lockwood 2018). Appeals to affects and the skillful use of material settings and devices (e.g. sports arenas or new media technologies), have for millennia been used by populists to successfully engage indifferent and indignant citizens in political processes - more recently also in the case of climate mitigation policies. Rethinking participation in light of the need to include the indifferent and indignant, I propose a non-populist approach to affective and material politics based on Nigel Thrift’s ‘intensities of feeling’ (2007), Jacques Rancière’s ‘redistribution of the sensible’ (2004), and Noortje Marres’ ‘material politics’ (e.g. 2011). Based on this theoretical foundation, the paper concludes

with a presentation of examples for innovative non-populist material and affective participation practices in the domain of urban and municipal climate mitigation planning.

Session Organizer:

Cian O’Donovan, University College London

490. Biopolitics, Gender, and Medicine in the 21st Century

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

The biopolitical terrain of gender and medicine has been reshaped in the 21st century by new knowledges, practices, and objects of inquiry. In this book forum, we bring together three newly released books on biopolitics, gender, and medicine and explore their substantive and methodological resonances. In *Feeling Medicine: How the Pelvic Exam Shapes Medical Training*, Kelly Underman explores how feminist lay and biomedical expert knowledges have reshaped in teaching and learning the pelvic exam in medical education. In *Freezing Fertility: Oocyte Cryopreservation and the Gender Politics of Aging*, Lucy van de Wiel analyses the widespread introduction of egg freezing and its consequences for the way in which female fertility and reproductive aging are understood, commercialized and politicized. In *Diagnosing Desire: Biopolitics and Femininity into the Twenty-First Century*, Alyson K. Spurgas examines the “new science of female sexuality” from a critical, sociological perspective, considering how today’s feminist-identified sex researchers study and manage women with low desire. For this session, we propose an author-meets-critics-style roundtable of our three books, facilitated by two critics. Each of the authors will present a short summary of our books and their relationship to the panel theme, followed by a thematic conversation led by our two critics. Positioning our books in relation to one another and the conference theme will invite scholarly discussion of what relations—good and bad—may emerge between contemporary biomedicine and gendered, racialised, and otherwise discursively coded and managed bodies and populations.

Participants:

Feeling Medicine: How the Pelvic Exam Shapes Medical Training *Kelly Underman, Drexel University*

Freezing Fertility: Oocyte Cryopreservation and the Gender Politics of Aging *Lucy van de Wiel, King’s College London*

Diagnosing Desire: Biopolitics and Femininity into the Twenty-First Century *Alyson K. Spurgas, Trinity College*

Session Organizers:

Kelly Underman, Drexel University

Alyson K. Spurgas, Trinity College

Lucy van de Wiel, King’s College London

Discussants:

Rene Almeling, Yale University

Miranda Waggoner, Florida State University

491. Inclusion and Its Consequences: The Politics of Diversity and Recognition in Health Data Projects - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

Engaging with the 4S 2021 conference theme, this panel explores the practices and consequences of data inclusion and exclusion in unequal worlds. We welcome empirical and conceptual papers examining health data projects of various scales, that consider some of the following questions: What are the various promises of diversity linked to data projects and how do these promises shape inclusion and exclusion practices, efforts, and outcomes? What are the tradeoffs and dilemmas inherent in and arising from narratives and practices of inclusion in health data projects? What are the drivers of activism around inclusion in health data and, alternatively, what drives resistance? How do current struggles for inclusion in health data today differ from demands for inclusion in the past? What sorts of visibilities and erasures might inclusion and exclusion in health data produce? This panel invites papers examining data assemblages and what it means to be counted (or not) in health data, to whom, and for what ends. Papers might address, for example, the inclusion or exclusion of various identifiers and statuses in state surveillance

systems, the participation or refusal of communities in health data repositories, interrogations of public and private institutions that seek to obscure data collection, and erasures and ethical challenges that arise as data emerge from and circulate across geographic scales from the local to the transnational.

Participants:

What do we ask of data? Inclusion and exclusion in the translational pipeline *Katherine M Hendy, University of Michigan*

The precision health movement is premised on the idea that treatment efficacy and safety can be improved through tailoring treatment recommendations at the individual level. Hidden within this mandate to individualize therapy is the empirical reality that recommendations are based on the assessments of population-level data. Thus, the individual becomes a constellation of populations—not just ethnicity and gender, but also treatment conditions and risk factors, which themselves can be sites of excursion and discrimination. While many precision health initiatives have been accompanied by mandates to include diverse populations in their biobanks and datasets, these efforts do not examine forms of exclusion that can happen as data moves through the translational pipeline and is developed to meet the needs of particular treatment populations with distinct risk factors. This paper will use the development of pharmacogenomic testing for psychotropic medications as a case study for examining the erasures that are produced as researchers and companies make decisions about how data is developed for use in medical practice. Pharmacogenomics for psychotropic medications is a particularly rich site for asking these questions for two reasons: First, the development of pharmacogenomics has been riddled with ethical debates about the appropriateness of different forms of racial and ethnic inclusion; second, psychiatric diagnoses have been continually shown to be susceptible to racial and ethnic bias. At the heart of this paper is an interrogation of the kinds of erasures that are produced through the questions that can be asked of data and the populations that are considered treatable.

The limits of uncertainty in genetic testing and diagnosis of neurodevelopmental disorders *Jen Marshall, University of Toronto*

Various investigations in science and technology studies (STS) have examined how clinicians and biomedical researchers understand and manage uncertainty. Approaches that fully engage with human biological complexity and its related uncertainties are generally considered more sophisticated than approaches that work to restrict complexity and uncertainty. However, some STS scholars have noted that biomedical discourses continue to divide people into restrictive ‘healthy’ and ‘normal’ spaces. Based on a study that critically examines genetics experts’ discourses, this presentation aims to explore how strategic uncertainty discourse expands inclusion criteria for neurodevelopmental disorder (NDD) testing and diagnosis and also frames who is ‘ethical’ in this context. By ethical, I refer to the construction of subjects whose management of uncertainty is considered ‘responsible’. For example, this presentation considers how uncertainty discourses associated with ‘big genetic data’ and new genetic technologies create possibilities to challenge diagnostic categories, open up traditional biomedical discourses to human biological diversity, and help emancipate the field from rigid certainties. Yet in this genetics context, the exploration of the unknown is often reserved for uncertainties associated with data generation and technological change, not the exploration of expanding ‘neurodevelopmental spaces’ for patients and their families. This presentation specifically considers the ways in which genetics experts present themselves as ethical adventurers in uncertainty when speaking about technological progress, while patients’ families’ explorations of diverse neurodevelopmental spaces are labeled unethical and

irresponsible. Uncertainty discourses in this context carry repercussions for patients and their families and how they might address genetic testing, NDD diagnosis and prognosis.

Who counts as family: A pluralistic account of family in the genetic context *Serene Ong*

Genetic testing is increasingly utilised as part of standard clinical care for patients with inheritable conditions. Notably, genetic information has unique aspects that present ethical challenges distinct from other types of medical information. Though generated in confidence to the patient, genetic test results are also of compelling interest to family members. However, disclosure relies on the patient revealing the information or consenting to the disclosure. The interests and preferences of family members may be excluded from consideration in decisions around disclosure, which may be unfair and lack justification. However, multiple understandings of family exist, which may result in misunderstandings and the exclusion of family that could have valid interests, particularly non-traditional forms not conventionally recognised as family. There is therefore a need to clarify who counts as family, and why. An understanding of who counts as family will have normative implications in clinical practice guidelines and policies regarding decisions surrounding genetic information, for instance in cascade screening. This paper reviews definitions of family relevant to the genetic context. Three aspects of family crucial in the genetic context are then discussed: biomedical, functional, and legal. Based on these aspects and a common limitation of existing definitions, I propose a pluralistic account of family that is inclusive and respectful of the various forms family can take.

Intersectionality at Its Limits: Public Health and the Epidemiology of Sexually Transmitted Infections *Mairead Sullivan, Loyola Marymount University*

As public health has taken up intersectionality as a gold standard theory, researchers tout intersectionality as a benchmark for validity of identity measures. Such a focus on identity markers in large scale data sets, however, confounds sexual health epidemiology. Sexual health epidemiology relies on an understanding of risk and risk practices that are not accounted for in demographic identity markers. In this paper, I explore the limits of intersectionality—specifically as intersectionality is named to measure and codify identity—for epidemiological understandings of sexually transmitted infection. Across the paper, I draw out a comparison between small scale, local efforts to curb HIV transmission and population based, large data set epidemiological studies of the herpes virus. My focus on the local explores how public health activists understand sexual behavior within social contexts. By contrast, population based, large data set epidemiological studies rely on comparisons across demographic groups. Such studies fail to engage the social context of sexual behavior. At root, I argue that public health scholarship that claims to newly engage intersectionality risks reifying dangerous ideas about race, gender, and sexual difference rather than interrogate the social systems that contextualize sexual practices. By contrast, local and activist public health efforts have been and remain remarkably good at harm reduction through understanding the social context of risk. Against intersectional public health’s promise to better attend to marginalized communities, I ask what is lost and what is risked when intersectionality is understood only through demographic data points.

Session Organizers:

Janet K. Shim, University of California, San Francisco
Sandra Soo-Jin Lee, Columbia University

492. Open Platforms: Technology, Politics, Business, and Social Movements in a Global Digital Age

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

Participants:

A Web of Knowledge for Well-Being in the Digital Age *Moritz Büchi, University of Zurich*

The promise of the digital age was to make the world's knowledge universally accessible, leading to empowerment and human flourishing. The promise appears to be broken—online activism serves the already powerful (Schradie, 2019), companies exploit digital traces (Richards & Hartzog, 2020). However, the idea of an epistemic web, or web of knowledge, is still alive (Renn, 2020; Hyman & Renn, 2017) and well-being is increasingly considered the objective of public policy (Frijters et al., 2020). This presentation outlines challenges in three separate fields contributing to “digital well-being” research—knowledge representation (how can the internet's networked knowledge potential be realized?), well-being economics (virtually no acknowledgement of digital ICTs' role in quality of life), and digital media use (a pathologizing focus on screen time and lack of theory). Meanwhile, public discourse is frequently occupied with equating digital ICTs with drugs and romanticizing the ostensible authenticity of pre-digital life. The project theorizes the conditions (e.g., technical and social) and pathways (e.g., through just-in-time knowledge acquisition) of digital ICT's positive effects on well-being. Thus, digital well-being is not an app; it is not about being happy with your smartphone use. Rather, digital well-being is a conceptual frame aiding the academic and public agenda to scrutinize the connections between “the digital” as a web of knowledge and well-being. I propose to not merge the digital and well-being—as the term “digital well-being” may imply—in order to assess subjective well-being under the condition of ubiquitous and abundant digital information and communication propositions.

Mumbuca Digital Community Currency: tools and practices configuring sociotechnical governances *Luiz Arthur Silva de Faria; Bruno Chapadeiro, UMEESP; Eduardo Diniz, Fundação Getúlio Vargas - EAESP*

This work deals with the problem of the implications of different ways of digitalizing the so-called social or community currencies (CCs) in Brazil. It starts from the following tension, verbalized by representatives of Brazilian Community Development Banks (CDBs): on the one hand, the digitization of social currencies would maintain “the same idea, [only] in different ways”; on the other hand, its governance would be nowadays “the most complex issue [for the Network of Banks]”. The investigation examines this tension in the case of the Mumbuca Digital CC (DCC) (in the city of Maricá, state of Rio de Janeiro), one of the greatest world DCC experiences (considering the amount of financial resources involved) and part of the Brazilian CDBs Network - which brings together more than 100 experiences. We collected data from 2015 until 2019, from semi-structured interviews, materials provided by the Mumbuca CDB, fieldnotes from an ethnographic research approach as well as through the Mumbuca DCC system administrative interface. The article advances in understanding DCCs, and particularly demonstrates that the materiality of the digital community currency is inseparable from the “social arrangement” around it. Precisely, using tools/concepts from the Actor Network Theory (such as translation, symmetry, networks, sociogram and technogram), we describe different moments of Mumbuca DCC, each one corresponding to different versions of CDBs principles and to different sociotechnical configurations of governance.

Performing Times: Temporalities in a Digital Currency *Ilan Talmud, University of Haifa, Israel*

Time and temporality are constitutive components of sociality in general and capitalism in particular (Braudel, 1984; Zerubavel, 1981; 1985; 2003; Lefebvre, 1992; Arrighi, 1994; Appadurai, 1996; Abbott, 1997; 2001; 2016; Castells, 2000; Sassen, 2000; Thrift, 2001; Birth, 2012; Beckert, 2015; 2017; Hammann and Suckert, 2018; Sharma, 2019; Beckert and Suckert, 2020. More

specifically, I show that temporal configurations are significant market devices for the social performance of digital socio-technological machineries (Knorr-Cetina & Preda, 2007; Jasanoff, 2015; Erenst, 2016; Wajzman, 2016;; Halawa, 2015; Wajzman & Dodd 2017; Serafim, 2019; Peoll, 2020). Further, I claim that sociological inquiry into digital temporalities reveals the “emergent grammar” hidden in cryptocurrencies. Accordingly, understanding time frames is a strategically efficacious window for the examining the mental ecology and the technical apparatus of digital materiality. Based on notions derived from communication theory, interactional socio-linguistics, literary theory, and recent models of the “sociology of the future”, I discuss four “time frames”, embedded in the sociotechnical imagery in and around cryptocurrencies. The first frame is “genesis” time, determining a priori the possible futures of the digital monetary value. The second is “transaction time”. The tension between cryptographic properties, transaction time cycle, scalability, and vested interests is the main engine behind the “civil wars” within the Bitcoin governance community, leading to internal splits (“forks”). A broader time horizon is the idealized future. The most dominant voices within the ecosystem around Blockchain community treat the technology as a magical remedy, delineating an evolutionary depiction of civilization, culminating in the institutionalization of the Blockchain as a solution for the current political economy's evils. The fourth time frame is “temporal integration”, a fusion of present and future tenses, where current valuation is derived from futurist idealized values, both morally and materially. Finally, I argue that understanding these time frames sheds light onto the construction and performance of blockchain technology and related digital financial innovations.

Reference Design as an Open Platform for Digital Technology of the Global South Market *Chen-Pang Yeang, University of Toronto; Wen-Ching Sung, University of Toronto; Zhixiang Cheng, University of Toronto*

The global mobile-device market reshuffled in the mid-2000s. Before, making cellular phones were monopolized by multi-nationals (e.g., Nokia, Motorola, and Sony-Ericsson), relying on licensed microchips from Californian enterprises like Qualcomm. In 2005-11, small Shenzhen-based companies featured low-ended brands and copycats that were cheap yet tailored to the local needs of low-income populations with innovative functional designs. This business model of poor people's phones succeeded in China, and spread to India, and Africa. A drive for this change was a new approach to mobile communication technology introduced by the Taiwanese IC design house MediaTek in 2004-05. MediaTek supplied cellular phones' hardware backbones as “reference designs.” Being cheap, ready to use, and unlicensed, the reference designs enabled firms with little capital and research-development capacity to make affordable phones. The story of MediaTek's reference designs is told in mass media and business scholarships as a facilitator of the copycat phenomenon or a case of disruptive innovation. In this paper, we examine the reference designs as an open platform characterizing the Global South's technological landscape. Their pluggable features black-boxed the hardware kernel and transformed phone-making into matters of determining functionality and user-interfaces and assembling. This open platform did not depend only upon standards and ready-made hardware. To make the solution work, MediaTek provided an array of services to phone makers from testing to marketing and logistics. To MediaTek members, such backstage work embodied an engineering culture distinguishing from Western enterprises like Qualcomm: strengths in labor-intensive elements to compensate for insufficiencies in advanced technology.

The challenges of building a weird object: first steps of a University Community Development Banks *Rodrigo Mendes Palmeira, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ);*

Vinicius Souza, Federal University of Rio de Janeiro; Luiz Arthur Silva de Faria; Alberto Jorge Silva de Lima, Celso Suckow da Fonseca Federal Centre of Technological Education; Filipe Silva

In dialogue with references from Science and Technology Studies (STS), especially the so-called Actor-network Theory or Sociology of Translation, this paper aims to narrate the making of entanglements, concerns, acceptance and strangeness encountered by those who have been working to stabilize a proposition located in the Technology Center of the Federal University of Rio de Janeiro (UFRJ), namely, a University Community Bank of Development. In our perspective, the Brazilian Community Development Banks (CDB) are networked solidarity financial services. Associative and communitarian initiatives, they are aimed at generating work and income in the perspective of reorganizing local economies, based on the principles of Solidarity Economy. Such proposition, inspired in the potentialization of the local economy in order to strengthen research and social inclusion initiatives, aroused strangeness, such as a supposed need for the proposal to be examined by the University's Law Department, or a characterization as a weird proposal when presented to a scientific society. It also aroused acceptance, such as from some of the university's undergraduate students, from the Brazilian Network of Community Banks (RBBC), from members of the solidarity economy movement, and from university laboratories. The project has a direct connection with the Informatics and Society research area at the Graduate Program in Systems Engineering and Computer Science (PESC/COPPE/UFRJ) and with the consolidation of university interaction between teaching, research and (specially) outreach activities in the Laboratory of Informatics and Society (Labis/PESC).

The promise and limitations of blockchains as open technology

Christopher Tozzi

The concept of openness in the realm of technology has been well established by initiatives such as open source software projects, efforts to define open standards and concerns with keeping the Internet "open." Against this historical backdrop, blockchain-based technologies both extend and problematize traditional understandings of open technology. On the one hand, blockchains promise a level of user participation and freedom from centralized governance that is unprecedented, even within other technological ecosystems that prize principles of openness. On the other hand, however, problems such as the ability of some actors to exercise outsize influence over blockchain networks, as well as the anonymity of participants in many blockchain communities, make it more difficult in some respects to pursue the goals traditionally associated with open technology. Using several blockchain platforms and communities as case studies, this paper examines the extent to which blockchains in general may be considered a form of open technology from both a technical as well as a social, cultural and political perspective.

Session Organizer:

Chen-Pang Yeang, University of Toronto

493. Building a new heuristic: knowledge production processes in interaction II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Participants:

Co-Creating Structural Change – A Need For Governance?

Anita Thaler, IFZ - Interdisciplinary Research Centre for Technology, Work and Culture; Magdalena Wicher, IHS (Institute for Advanced Studies, Vienna); Sandra Karner, IFZ - Inter-University Research Center for Technology, Work and Culture

The idea of co-creation as a means of knowledge production is

increasing in different spheres of research practices and STS in particular. In our projects, we implement co-creation to use interaction processes with a variety of different actors for reaching structural and institutional change towards more (gender) equal and sustainable science and research. To enlarge the impact on science and research policy and funding, we not only interact with researchers on different levels but also work together with research funding organisations (RFOs) and policy actors. Policies are constructed by social processes and scientists shape and co-produce STI policy themselves. This knowledge is not new (e.g. Gieryn 1995; Latour 1987; Jasanoff 1990), but the role of governance and policy development are underexposed in their impact on shaping those processes of knowledge production, the relationships various actors can perform and which methods and practices are implemented and rewarded. In our paper we want to present two approaches in co-creating knowledge with RFOs to reach the goal of structural change by (1) setting up communities of practices (CoPs; Karner et al. 2014) and (2) using methods inspired by the PIPA (Participatory Impact Pathways Analysis, Douthwaite et al. 2009) approach. We will focus on the stakeholder involvement process with research funding and policy actors and share key insights from 20 interviews, which set the basic trust for follow-up activities (stakeholder workshops etc.). These activities should lead to co-created policy papers with an impact on governance structures that support structural change.

Ethnography and policy: Knowledge production as negotiating multiplicity in landscapes of policy practice *Michaela Spencer, Charles Darwin University; Natalie Gill, Freelance*

In this presentation, we draw on our experience of teaching 'policy and ethnography' to students who were also employed as government bureaucrats working in remote Aboriginal communities in northern Australia. Initially, we draw on our own experiences as STS researchers working in policy landscapes shaped by multiple discourses that included subjectivities, objects and contexts that were at times uncomfortable or excluding. We share stories of ethnographic research practice where we position our own collaborative engagements, and those of the student's engagement in the institutions of government bureaucracy and the institutions and knowledge practices of Indigenous people-places. In foregrounding ethnographic stories as actors in these complex policy landscapes, and mobilising a working typology ('figures', 'tensions', 'located subjects' and 'materialities'), we've reached towards ways that student-researchers can work with their own embodied participation in the configuring networks of policy practice to generate research accounts which do not abstract or step away from the situations of their involvement, but nonetheless produce robust policy data, and generative research outcomes.

Fanwork is Fam work: Creating Diverse Meaning of Disability through Tagging Practices *Catherine Duchastel, STS Program, York University*

Fanworks are creative works based on existing media texts fans create for their own and other fans' pleasure. Fanworks can both be defined by the transformative and intertextual engagements with these existing media texts, but by the rich and varied personal interactions between fans, and within fandom (Busse, 2017). Through conversations, exchanges between creators and supporters of fanworks, and involvement with the shaping and maintaining of fanfiction spaces, fans have created their own knowledge about gender, sexuality, and consent (Becque, 2012; Meggers, 2012; Neville 2018; Popova, 2017; Warburton, 2010). This presentation, based on my doctoral research, will examine how fans authors create multiple discourses of disability through the creation of freeform tagging, and the practice of using multiple tags on Archive Of Our Own. Tags are words and phrases that are used as metadata in fanfiction archives in order to describe and organize fanworks. AO3 uses both an informal freeform tagging process that allows fans to generate their own

tags, and a formalized tagging organization maintain by fans. Both are used on individual fanworks uploaded to AO3 to communicate information to potential readers about the content they can expect to find therein. Tagging practices on AO3 thus serve as a way to create folksonomies about particular subjects, including disability. Tagging practices about disability both reify accepted knowledge about disability as a biological or medical fact and challenge it by the creation of new and multiple definition of disability as empowering, pleasurable, complex, funny, and desirable.

From the Collaboration Network to the Process of Scientific Practices of Astrophysicists in Mexico *Christian Jonathan Poblete-Trujillo, Universidad Autónoma Metropolitana-Azcapotzalco, México*

The aim of this presentation is to analyze the co-production of knowledge of astrophysicists in Mexico. Two analytical axes are developed. The first axis describes the structure of the collaboration network of astrophysicists attached to two research institutes in Mexico about Astrophysics: the National Institute of Astrophysics, Optics and Electronics (INAOE, by its acronym in Spanish) a public research center, and the Institute of Radioastronomy and Astrophysics (IRyA) belonging to the National Autonomous University of Mexico (UNAM). The second axis investigates the scientific practices during the process of knowledge production in the scientific collaborations of astrophysicists from the two institutes mentioned. The research is carried out through a mixed method: quantitative analysis of co-authorship networks (scientometrics), bibliometric visualization tools (Pajek and VOSViewer), and semi-structured qualitative interviews. Quantitative network analysis is used to identify centrality measures and epistemic communities of the collaborative networks of researchers from both institutes at a macro and meso level. For which the articles indexed in SCOPUS in the period 2015-2019 are retaken. Subsequently, with the interviews, the scientific practices of astrophysicists are deepened, which includes from the interactions between the different actors, to the cognitive and technological aspects that were used to produce knowledge throughout the process of scientific collaboration.

Traveling texts: Where Women Have Our Bodies, Ourselves *Lillian Walkover, University of California, San Diego*

Women's health has long been a key arena for the production and distribution of counter-hegemonic narratives about bodies, agency, and power. The global travels of the seminal health manuals *Where Women Have No Doctor* and *Our Bodies Ourselves*, analyzed through the lens of postcolonial STS, trace a path through intersecting locations and languages, in some cases diverging and in others showing up inside the same adapted text – because, as I argue, they address related but distinct approaches to ideas of subjects, access, and empowerment. Their production and travels also reflect the epistemologies of social movements simultaneously replicating and working hard to reimagine gendered and (post)colonial power dynamics. This paper draws on 63 interviews with participants involved in the translation, adaptation, distribution, and use of *Where There Is No Doctor* and related texts, including *Where Women Have No Doctor*, into Tamil, Kannada, Hindi, and English, for use in India, 6 pilot interviews with participants working on adaptations for other parts of Asia, Africa, and the Americas, and archival research on *Our Bodies Ourselves* in the Boston Women's Health Book Collective Records at the Schlesinger Library of the Radcliffe Institute for Advanced Study at Harvard University. Together, the travels of these texts – and the people who create, adapt, and translate them – tell an important story about what it means to create and access the resources needed for health, and the ability of people to act on information when it is provided to them in a clear and usable format.

Session Organizer:

Mariela Bianco Bozzo, Universidad de la Republica

494. Optical Media: The Impact of Visual Technologies - IV

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Optical media, borrowed from Friedrich Kittler, is an expanded concept that connects photography, film and television with other techniques and technologies that mediate optics and vision (e.g. microscopes, telescopes, oscilloscopes, echocardiography, ad inf.). Normalized, expected and often desired, optical media shape how we perceive the reality that surrounds us, mediating our understanding and experience of our inter- and intra-relationships with ourselves, others, objects, and worlds. In so doing, they constitute power relationships that reify inequalities and uncertainties, the key themes of 4S 2021, rendering certain people, places, and things visible, invisible, or hypervisible. These issues have grown in importance in the wake of COVID-19 and social distancing, where optical media have become ubiquitous. This panel welcomes interdisciplinary research from STS and neighbouring fields that critically examine the role of these embedded and disruptive technologies in guiding our world views and relationships. By paying attention to the modes of seeing and looking that shape our perceptions, behaviours, and practices we can begin to better address their effects on other information systems including but not limited to the ones we work in, socialize in, and reside in. Questions we ask include how are modes of looking shaped by digital optical media? What potentials are there for visual manipulation, exploitation, or psychological vulnerabilities? What new possibilities for ways of thinking, interacting or organizing information do these technologies offer? Who and what is being rendered visible, invisible, or hypervisible and the power politics of optical media?

Participants:

Mars as Frontier: Optical Media and Visions of Colonization
Piotr Szpunar, University at Albany, SUNY

Mars has long been a screen onto which humans project futures. How Mars is imagined changes alongside the optical media directed at its surface: a god of war (the human eye), a world of canals constructed by intelligent beings struggling to survive (telescopic photography); a planet of seasonal vegetation (Earth-based spectrography); a barren desert-like planet (flyby photography), and so on. Today, Mars is imagined as a frontier, a place to tame, exploit, and settle: from SpaceX's planned 2026 manned-mission (and "Colonize Mars" t-shirts), to Mike Pence's promise to put "American boots on the face of Mars," to the United Arab Emirate's envisioned 2117 colony of 100,000. Today's dominant optical medium trained on the Red Planet: orbital and in situ spectrometers/spectrometers. Spectrometers observe how matter interacts with electromagnetic radiation. The interactions—attuned to specific wavelengths (e.g., UV light)—produce emission and absorption spectra unique to a given element, allowing scientists to identify the makeup of soil, rock, and atmosphere. In relation to Mars, this work involves machine calibration, visualization software, a trained human eye, lab-generated spectra, Earth-analog site observation, and in situ photography. How is mediated scientific exploration enlisted in rendering Mars visible as frontier? Might it facilitate a way to see Mars otherwise? This paper addresses these questions by examining NASA's Perseverance Rover and its dual objectives of searching for signs of past microbial life and uncovering resources for future human missions. The possibilities are overlapping and in tension, signaling how spectroscopy, situated within cultural, organizational, and political assemblages, might be used to both reinforce narratives of colonization and facilitate a radical rethinking of humankind's relation to the non-human cosmos.

Epistemic Value of (mis)Alignments Between Tracking Devices, Birds and Ecologists *Selen Eren, University of Groningen; Anne Beaulieu, University of Groningen*
More-than-human relationships in ecology are at the core of knowledge production about bird migration and potential future

survival. We use a lens of 'care' to analyze how birds, satellite tracking devices, and ecologists form material and affective entanglements when they meet in the creation and maintenance of knowledge through sensing infrastructures. We look at how encounters between them make sensing birds, devices, and ecologists possible. Specifically, we focus on the following encounters: ecologists handling and tagging birds, birds meeting devices, devices functioning in infrastructures, and infrastructures scaffolding ecologists. This presentation is based on empirical data collected during our collaboration with the global flyway ecology group based at the University of Groningen. By studying complex interactions in the knowledge infrastructure at hand, we make explicit which types of technozoological, anthrozoological, and sociotechnical alignments are needed to produce credible knowledge claims. The paper puts three bodies of work in dialogue: (1) the feminist STS literature committed to the epistemic value of care practices in research (Puig de la Bellacasa 2011, Friese 2013), (2) the literature that focuses on sensing technologies and the power relations/asymmetries revealed or exacerbated with them (Gabrys 2018, Howe 2019), and (3) the STS literature that lays the ground for interventionist discussions around knowledge and data infrastructures (Edwards et al. 2013, Baker & Karasti 2018).

Session Organizers:

Alexander Monea, George Mason University

Paula Sanchez Nunez de Villavicencio, University of Toronto

495. Out of Breath, Out of Body, Out of Food, and Out of this World: Explorations of Life's Limits in the Twentieth Century
 11:30 to 1:00 pm
 4S 2021 Virtual: 15

This panel explores scientific and technical re-creations of new and extreme environments that revealed the boundaries of life. From deep mines, to the upper atmosphere, to earth-bound models of space stations and alien worlds, our Panel expands and connects histories of the human sciences and the environment, with astrobiology, mining, the military, and NASA. In those overlapping fields of interest, the creation of new knowledge about extreme environments and time itself can be understood. Further, the Panel's papers reveal how life's limits were conceptualized and made experimental, revealing not only unforeseen knowledge about new environments but also unexpected insights into ideas and experiences of time and reality itself.

Participants:

Military Models of Life on Mars: The Cold War Politics of early USAF Astrobiology *Jordan Bimm, University of Chicago*

When U.S. Air Force scientist Hubertus Strughold began simulating life-on-Mars he wasn't animated by lofty questions like "are we alone?" or "what is the origin of life on Earth?" He was interested in the limits of life and securing Mars for U.S. military operations in the burgeoning Cold War. In 1956, Strughold constructed a set of airtight jars capable of replicating the harsh conditions believed to exist on the surface of Mars: a thin nitrogen rich atmosphere, arid soil, and freezing nights. Then, he sealed hardy microbes and lichens inside to see if any could survive. The goal was to see if extraterrestrial life could be used to build a self-sustaining military base on the Red Planet. Strughold's "Mars Jars,"—as they were called in the press and by civilian exobiologists at NASA who adopted and promoted them in the 1960s—made Mars seem accessible, habitable, and strategic, another extreme environment for Cold War scientific and military intervention alongside polar regions, the deep seas, and Earth orbit. This paper explores the cultural work of Strughold's Mars Jars and the kinds of colonial, militaristic, and instrumentalist relationships to Mars and potential extraterrestrial life these types of experiments (now called Mars environmental simulators) continue to foster. Strughold's grisly obsession with the limits of life, and his absence from the origin story of modern

astrobiology, will be considered in the context of his previous work for the Luftwaffe and his connections to lethal human experiments on concentration camp prisoners during World War Two.

Living and Mining on the Border of Hell: Acclimatization Experiments on South Africa's Ultra-Deep Mines *Megan Eardley, Princeton University*

In the mid twentieth century, the world's deepest mines operated more than two miles below sea level. In South Africa, industry scientists developed an extensive acclimatization process to prevent lethal heat stress among miners that worked at these depths. To increase the efficiency of this process, the Human Sciences Laboratory developed a series of experimental "surface acclimatization chambers" to test and train the physiological response of new miners before they were cleared for underground work. At the same time, the Laboratory used these chambers to determine the point at which extreme heat and humidity would render the underground environment unworkable. Between 1953 and 1980, they conducted research that challenged the established limits of human physiology in high heat. This paper analyzes how the South African mining industry attempted to overcome the limits of the human body in unknown, and radically unstable underground environments. It attends to the way the design of the surface acclimatization chamber produced a bodily condition that cannot be sustained by biological processes. Finally, it addresses the organization of time in an industry that increasingly requires the dispossession of the miner's body as well as the earth.

Cultivating "Oxygen Sense": Hypobaric Exposure and the Phenomenology of High Altitude in the Royal Air Force 1939-1945 *James Joseph Esposito, The Ohio State University*

Devastating losses inflicted upon the Royal Air Force by the German Luftwaffe in the Battle of France displayed the woeful inadequacy of the British approach to aviation medicine and high altitude warfare in 1939-1940. RAF airmen refused oxygen masks due to discomfort and fierce skepticism of altitude's deleterious effect on human performance. The cognitive effects of attenuated air remained largely imperceptible and frequently dismissed by flyers. Wide adoption of oxygen masks was not simply a matter of design or training, but required an embodied knowledge of the sub-stratospheric environment at 20,000 feet. Lacking electronic oxygen sensors, the RAF Physiological Laboratory cultivated aircrew to sense hypoxia's onset within hypobaric chambers. Rarefied air created a kind of cognitive interference of 'being-in-the-anoxic' crew could experience and observe directly, using their own experience as foreknowledge of hypoxia's incapacitating potential in flight. Running counter to trends in sensory history which correlate the diminished importance of non-visual senses (smell, touch) with modernity, this paper argues for a new wartime "oxygen sense" created through technology and militarization of Earth's extremes. New sensory awareness reinforced the value of supplemental oxygen and provided flyers with valuable tacit knowledge to improve combat performance and safety. Chamber knowledge firmly established altitude's capacity to distort the human mind, easing the integration of human and machine in the skies over Western Europe during the Second World War.

Far Beyond The Moon: Life Support Systems in the Space Age *David Munns, John Jay College of Criminal Justice, CUNY*

Throughout the depressed 1970s and into the energized 1980s, the quest to perfect long-term life support to live in space remained one of NASA's near continuous projects as the agency moved from Skylab through the space shuttle and the planning for space station Freedom. To realize Freedom necessitated the inclusion of a total life support system to maintain a habitable environment. Because a space station would receive and launch people on a continuous basis, NASA addressed the requirement

of a working “environmental control/regenerative life support” system. The all-too salient political and social overtones of America’s failure to deploy Freedom opens new windows to the historical connections between maintenance and habitability. As this talk argues, the concepts and working models of closed environment life support explored during Freedom’s planning was understood as really the next in a series of test modules working always towards a permanent space station and untethered Mars missions.

Session Organizer:

James Joseph Esposito, The Ohio State University

496. Unpacking biosocial approaches to stress & trauma - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

This panel will bring together scholars researching trauma and stress from biosocial perspectives. Trauma-informed approaches are often positioned as a gold standard of care across biomedical, therapeutic, carceral and policy domains. Historical trauma frameworks have long been central to collective identity and politics among Indigenous, Black and other racially marginalised communities, and have gained momentum through recent anti-racist and anti-colonial movements like Black Lives Matter and Idle No More. Research fields like social epidemiology, critical public health and biological anthropology have explored how trauma and stress “get inside” the body to shape health disparities (e.g. “minority stress”; “weathering” [Geronimus 1992]). Recently, research on the developmental origins of health and disease and epigenetics is redefining trauma as an exposure with a heritable trace (Dubois&Guaspare 2020), raising new questions about ancestral memory and reproductive politics. We invite scholars from various disciplines to explore how trauma and stress are enacted biosocially through human experience, activist tactics, government policy and scientific knowledge. How are trauma and stress defined, studied and reformulated across these arenas? What are the social and political stakes of trauma-informed practices? What forms of temporality, identity and justice do they produce?

Participants:

Trauma Induced Dementia and Rendering the Biosocial Molar
Greg Hollin

There is a growing belief that at least some Alzheimer’s-like dementias need to be understood in environmental, rather than simply genetic, terms. In this reimagining, “trauma” is articulated as key to understanding dementia and, in particular, brain trauma emerges as a key risk factor. This focus upon trauma and dementia can be understood as part of a broader biosocial “turn” within the biomedical sciences, a turn that has seen a refiguring of the relationship between “nature” and “culture.” The practises of the “new biologies,” such as epigenetics and neuroplasticity, have been strongly implicated in this turn, as have a variety of sociological consequences, not least the ‘molecularisation of biography and milieu’ (Niewöhner, 2011). It is here that trauma-induced dementias depart from many other conditions mapped in the contemporary biosocial field, for the “environmental” cause here appears resolutely molar – not intracellular but the car crash, the battlefield, or the abusive household – while “trauma” is not figured as embodied and intergenerational but as a blunt, external force. Discussing my ethnographic work with neuropathologists, molecular neuroscientists, and sport scientists, I here consider if and how the sciences of trauma-induced neurodegenerative disease complement existing work theorising the emerging biosocial sciences. I, first, suggest that in continuing to conceptualise both the environment and trauma in molar terms, trauma-induced neurodegeneration complicates work that takes molecularisation as its point of departure for theorising the “new biologies” and, second, draw attention to a quite different and ongoing politics of life consolidating around environmental dementias.

Semantic mining and tinkering: neuroepigenetic figurations of trauma
Elsher Lawson-Boyd, Deakin Univeristy

The life sciences have undergone some fascinating changes over the last two decades. Doxa pertaining to DNA - such as its functioning as the “master code” of life - have been challenged by postgenomic sciences, particularly by the field of epigenetics (Keller 1997, 2002). Fundamental to epigenetic thinking is the idea that environments not only act as mediators of gene expression, but as exposures, which dictates that anything from food to green-house gas to stress can be potentially noxious when ingested, absorbed or inflicted. Adding the prefix “neuro”, neuroepigenetics arrives at the intersection of neuroscience and epigenetics, an emerging field which investigates how environmental influences may cause epigenetic modifications in neurons and in turn, affect their function, lifespan and importantly, their capacity to retain memory – not only in an individual sense but across generations (Day & Sweatt 2011). Although still in its infancy, the kinds of questions being asked in neuroepigenetics (i.e. how environments get under the skull) are in need of feminist STS engagement and active participation. The discursive dimensions of epigenetic research have been robustly considered (Kenney & Müller 2017; Richardson 2017; Saldaña-Tejeda 2018; Warin & Hammarström, 2018), yet the ways in which terms like trauma and stress are complicated by neuroepigenetics require further attention. Drawing from peer reviewed neuroepigenetic articles and interviews with leading neuroepigenetic researchers, this paper explores two questions: what kind of bodies and traumas are enacted in neuroepigenetics (Mol 2012; 2002), and how might these ontologies lend themselves to figurations of trauma that are materially and semiotically “otherwise”? If collaboration across the bio and social sciences leads to thicker figurations of trauma, then this exploration welcomes a “new feminist analysis” of nervous tissue (Roy 2016: 534), where semantic tinkering can support generative constructions of biosocial difference and give trauma agential, material and temporal weight.

Re-enacting Trauma in the Lab. On Environmental Epigenetics and the Molecularisation of Mental Health
Georgia Samaras, Munich Center for Technology in Society, Technical University of Munich

Psychiatry defines trauma as the highest form of stress, commonly understood as the event that precipitates a post-traumatic stress disorder (PTSD). However, PTSD does not occur in all people who experienced something devastating. Therefore, psychiatrists propose that some seem to be more resilient to the effects of trauma than others. The reasons behind this divergence, however, remain widely unknown. Against this background, environmental epigenetics is increasingly informing trauma-research with the hope to deliver molecular answers. Based on ethnographic fieldwork in two laboratories, I investigate how trauma is enacted biomedically in different research arrangements with equally different implications for how we can understand and possibly treat mental health conditions. By focussing on cohort studies and mouse models, I will trace how trauma comes to matter differently in these research arrangements: from “naturalistic” forms of stress harnessed ex post facto for the laboratory to standardised re-enactments of traumatic experiments. These enactments also direct the researchers’ ideas about where to situate trauma as something that is embodied in molecular structures: assuming that epigenetics is a form of biological memory, in which tissue do researchers imagine to explore epigenetic traces of atrocity? The aim of my presentation is, firstly, to provide a fine-grained analysis of how certain decisions in epigenetic stress research enact particular research objects (trauma/stress) in specific ways that are bound to the experimental setting itself. Secondly, I intend to show how these decisions produce different scientific stories (Kenney, 2015) on the phenomenon in question, that is, mental health.

Stress as an Ecological Disturbance: Interrogating the Connections between the Microbiome, Stress and Obesity

Azita Chellappoo, Ruhr University Bochum

Over the past two decades there has been a rapidly developing interest in the human microbiome. Scholars have highlighted the ways in which this ‘probiotic turn’ (Lorimer 2020) initiates (or carries the potential to initiate) shifts in conceptions of the self, biological citizenship, biological-social boundaries, and modes of governance. I analyse key scientific studies to draw out the ways in which microbiome research characterises stress and its relationship to the gut microbiome and obesity, through changes within the gut-brain axis. I argue that in this context stress becomes understood as a perturbation of an ecological community that includes the host and various microbes. I chart the avenues this could provide for expanding relations of causation, responsibility and intervention beyond the body, and more fully grasping how biological and social processes are intertwined (which remains important in the context of the stalemate between obesity science and critical fat studies (Warin 2015)). Whilst a deeper understanding of our microbial entanglements carries this potential, a closer look at scientific practice troubles any straightforwardly optimistic narrative. Firstly, microbiome studies problematically position obesity as a kind of trauma response in itself. This deserves particular attention in the context of the strong ‘translational imperative’ (Huss 2014) that could change the way that obese bodies are managed. Secondly, I build on previous analyses (e.g., Benezra 2020) to suggest ways that this work struggles to capture the role of structural discrimination in producing microbiome difference, tending to individualise and biomedicalize the drivers of health inequalities.

Checklist Medicine: Managing the Traumatized Identity in Difficult to Diagnose Health Conditions *Alli Morgan, Icahn School of Medicine at Mount Sinai*

Notions of trauma have come to penetrate how pathology, time, and suffering are governed, named, and medicalized. While the proliferation of trauma-informed practice has opened up a hopeful possibility for understanding bodies in relation to environments, histories, and structural conditions oft left out of US medical practice, the expansive clinical identification of trauma presents double-binds for patients. Despite growing social and clinical recognition of the ways trauma manifests in very “real” ways, patients with histories of trauma are still subject to intense marginalization within medicine. Those with contested health conditions often feel these tensions most acutely, as expansive understandings of trauma mean that it often becomes a default, totalizing explanatory category for that which cannot be explained via other, conventionally biomedically sanctioned, means. Drawing upon three years of ethnographic fieldwork with patients with contested illnesses in the US healthcare system and auto-ethnographic work on medical education, this paper examines the ways in which patients and clinicians negotiate tensions between formal nosological and embodied experiences of trauma. For many patients, histories of trauma—while salient sites for intrasubjective examination—must be strategically managed in the clinical arena. Describing how physicians are taught to elicit histories of trauma via the clinical interview—typically via a “checklist”—this paper attempts to describe the ways in which broad and uncritical attention to trauma further compounds challenges for patients seeking care.

Session Organizers:

Jaya Keaney, Deakin University
Megan Warin, University of Adelaide
Emma Kowal, Deakin University
Henrietta Byrne, The University of Adelaide

Chair:

Emma Kowal, Deakin University

Discussant:

Elizabeth Roberts, University of Michigan

497. Splinternets - III: State and Market

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Conflating Computing Characters in Cookie Controversies *Meg Leta Jones, Georgetown University*

The cookie banner is an image that hides a splinternet divided by distinct cultural, legal, and technical controversies between the U.S. and EU. Accounts of digital consent begin in the mid-1990s in Silicon Valley, arguing that using consent to control personal information was fine for the good old analog days but could not hold up to the information overload brought on by the internet. According to this framing, digital consent is an information management problem that needs to be fixed by making terms easier to read or easier to understand or more simple to change. This project offers a different history of the cookie that starts in the 1960s in many cities on both sides of the Atlantic. It argues that the internet did not break digital consent - digital consent was created for the internet. Building on Ian Hacking’s Making Up People, I trace the distinct histories of three “computing characters” made up by Western technology governance processes: the data subject in data protection law, the anonymous user in communication privacy law, and the privacy consumer in consumer protection law. I collect, organize, and analyze a number of archival materials from www-talk developer forums and IETF standards to legislative hearings and agency committee meetings using a legal construction of technology approach to parse out the diverse origins and evolutions of these characters. To unpack the cookie banner is to untangle these different characters who have different technical, political, and commercial histories but have been conflated through transatlantic negotiations.

Global Corporations, National Laws: Data Access Requests in India, USA, and UK *Justin Petelka; Megan Finn, University of Washington; Elisa Oreglia, King's College London; Janaki Srinivasan, International Institute of Information Technology - Bangalore; Janani A P, IIIT Bangalore*

Multinational Internet corporations operate global platforms. However, as they widely publicize, corporations adhere to national laws related to data protection, privacy and content control. Furthermore, even as national laws about the Internet vary, the ways in which these laws are interpreted by corporations and enacted in their digital infrastructures also vary. Thus, the variation of laws as well as the interpretation of national laws by Internet companies can make many internets. This paper reports on an effort to understand how local internet laws are interpreted by corporations, designed and implemented in technical systems, and experienced by users. Specifically, we examine the process of acquiring one’s data about online activities from corporations in the USA, UK (pre-Brexit), and India. We also address the effect of the EU-based GDPR regulations on policy and information technology outside of the EU, with a focus on post-colonial influences. While differing national laws suggest splinternets, some observe the GDPR beyond EU borders as companies comply with laws in one jurisdiction and apply the same technology to citizens in other countries. In this study we worked with 19 people across the three regions who made a total of 38 data access requests between 2019 and 2020. Through this work, we address two questions: 1) How do national laws shape the experience of “the Internet,” particularly as it pertains to data access requests? And 2) How are national data access request laws variously interpreted by corporations and experienced by data subjects?

Internet Fragmentation? Renationalisation and new forms of authoritarian globalization *Julia Pohle, WZB Berlin Social Science Center; Daniel Voelsen, German Institute for International and Security Affairs*

The Internet still holds the promise of uniting all people in a global communication network. But in recent years, various governments have been trying to subordinate the Internet – including both the layer of its technical infrastructure as well as its applications – to the system of the Westphalian state order. Western policy-makers and observers, in turn, have raised concerns about a potential fragmentation of the Internet on a technical, economic and regulatory level. This paper questions the idea of Internet fragmentation and argues instead that the current developments are part of a contestation process which may ultimately pave the way for a new form of authoritarian globalization. The paper takes its conceptual starting point in network theory which it proposes as an alternative analytical lens to study changes regarding the Internet infrastructure as well as configurations of actors and power in global Internet governance. Drawing on this theoretical foundation and on existing historical research, the paper retraces the conflicts and developments that shaped the Internet since the Internet exceptionalists' visions in the 1990s until states' recent pursuits of digital sovereignty. It identifies three phases which are characterized by particular network configurations regarding 1) the internet infrastructure, 2) the digital economy, 3) the digital public sphere, and 4) Internet governance and regulation. With this reconstruction, the paper connects existing STS scholarship on infrastructures with research on Internet governance and on the digital economy, thereby providing a more comprehensive perspective on the changing nature of the Internet as a global digital network.

Session Organizer:

Elisa Oreglia, King's College London

Discussant:

Ashwin Jacob Mathew, King's College London

498. Making Early Career Researchers' Voices Heard for Gender Equality III: Intersectional Discriminations in STEM

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 18

This final session offers different national perspectives on discriminations experienced by Early Career Researchers in the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics field through an intersectional lens. Drawing from their study or their personal experience, speakers explore the effects of overlapping discriminations (based on ethnicity, caste, religion, gender identity, language) on the scientists' life.

Participants:

A Global Approach To The Gender Gap In Mathematical, Computing, And Natural Sciences: *Colette GUILLOPE*, Université Paris-Est Créteil; *Marie-Françoise Roy*, Université de Rennes 1

Our aim is to present the achievements of a three-year project (2017-2019) [1,2] funded by the International Science Council, including eleven partners working together, precisely eight international unions in all disciplines of Mathematical, Computing, and Natural Sciences, UNESCO, and two non-governmental organizations in gender. This is the first study of this amplitude ever done. Three different methodologies have been used: a global survey of women and men scientists with more than 32,000 responses; an investigation of gender patterns in millions of scientific publications; and the setting-up of a best-practice database of initiatives that address the gender gap in STEM at various levels. As a whole, we observed that the gender gap is very real in mathematics and science. Women's experiences are consistently less positive, regardless of discipline, geographical zone, and level of development. Furthermore, women remain underrepresented as authors in the most renowned journals. On a positive note, the gender productivity gap has been closing since 1970. We shall especially report on early careers researchers. The only part which is the same for women and men is the time and the way the subject of study is being chosen. Otherwise, women tend to have a

mountain of discriminations to climb. [1] Gender Gap in Science Project <https://gender-gap-in-science.org/> [2] A Global Approach to the Gender Gap in Mathematical, Computing, and Natural Sciences: How to Measure It, How to Reduce It? (C. Guillopé, M.-F. Roy eds.), 2020.

https://zenodo.org/record/3882609#.X0Q0CIDgo_U

Women in Science and Engineering in South Asia *Roli Varma*, University of New Mexico

I will present a cross-national perspective of science and engineering (S&E) education and employment among women in selected South Asian countries. A cross-national perspective means examining the status of women along with certain indicators across national borders; thus, it differs from the case study of a country. The increasing representation of women in some S&E fields in South Asian societies in the last decade has opened "new horizons" by widening the empirical base for a comparative understanding. By examining similarities and differences among women in S&E in different national settings, I will identify a number of commonly shared attributes as well as differences which will shed new light on the old question: what can be done to make S&E gender-inclusive in South Asia? Considering South Asian countries have numerous divisions along the lines of caste, class, ethnicity, language, and religion, I will address intersectionality, that is, to take women's overlapping identities and experiences in order to understand the interwoven bias they face in S&E.

The Effect Of Intersectional Discrimination Experiences On The Scientists' Life *Antonia Velicu*, Universität Zürich; *Julia Jerke*, University of Zurich; *Heiko Rauhut*, Universität Zürich

Even though discrimination in science has been in the focus of research for some time, it is still widely unknown how intersectional discrimination experiences affect scientific work and collaborations. Originally conceptualized by Crenshaw (1988), intersectionality was intended to capture the multitude of discrimination. Building on previous inequality research, we implement an extended version of the diversity wheel in a large-scale survey with 15'778 scientists across all disciplines from Germany, Austria and Switzerland. Almost half of the respondents state that they have experienced disadvantages at least once in their career, with scientists that identify with the third gender experiencing the most discrimination (71%), followed by women (57%), and men experiencing the least (37%). 57% of all respondents with such experiences have been discriminated based on more than one diversity dimension, again with women and the third sex being more affected. Preliminary results further show that, regardless of the gender, experiencing discrimination has a strong impact on the everyday life as a scientist. Respondents who faced disadvantages report more frequent and more stressful conflicts with co-authors as well as a tougher competition and a less collegial atmosphere, on the one hand, and fewer training and career opportunities on the other hand. Strikingly, these effects are substantially amplified when we consider respondents that have made discrimination experiences based on more than one trait, underlining the importance of research on intersectional discrimination. Our findings, therefore, provide valuable insights on how (intersectional) discrimination affects science in general along with working conditions and collaborations in particular.

Being a Feminist Physicist Ethnographer: Exploring Diversity and Inclusion through Identity Work *Mirjam Fines-Neuschild*, Université de Montréal

For over than four years, I studied my foster/present Physics Department at Université de Montréal looking at social mechanisms involved in the under-representation of women in physics only to realize that my research work was about my own identity struggles being a female physicist, a mother since 2016, a white francophone, a third-generation immigrant, a daughter of

two Protestant ministers and an unspoken identity. Women are under-represented in physics (APS, 2019). Through the extensive set of studies, we – as a feminist community – revealed the multiple structural obstacles imposed on scientists of historically marginalized identities. To deepen our understanding, I look at multiple aspect of the life in physics: departmental culture, particle physics research, departmental committee on diversity. I carried on an ‘at-home’ ethnography (Alvesson, 2008). As a woman physicist/ethnographer, I observed, took field notes, draw, interviewed members of the diversity committee, ran through multiple documents, recorded one of my own conferences on physics research, started and gave up a blog, etc. I am engaged in fostering Equity, Diversity, and Inclusion (EDI) in universities. I cofounded a physics diversity committee and showed through my research how it affects positively the departmental community. I am an active member of a University Québec Network for EDI (RIQÉDI) which inspired me to publish an article on excellence, EDI and scholarships (Fines-Neuschild & Pulido, 2021). Also, I am a facilitator for the American Physical Society EDI where I assist with great enthusiasm five teams from Canada and Finland in their EDI efforts.

Session Organizer:

Areti Damala, CNRS and ENS - REPUBLIQUE DES SAVOIRS -PROJET ACT

Chair:

Chloé Mour, CNRS USR 3608

Discussant:

Anne-Sophie Godfroy, République des savoirs (CNRS, École Normale Supérieure, Collège de France)

499. Carson Prize Session

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

The Carson Prize is awarded annually for a book in Science and Technology Studies with distinctive social and political relevance. Both single and multi-authored books are eligible if they represent original work. This session celebrates the 2021 winner.

Session Organizer:

Olivia Doggett, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

Chair:

María Belén Albornoz, FLACSO Latin American Social Studies Faculty

500. Biometrics on the Move - IV

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

Biometric practices have moved around the world through colonial and postcolonial contexts, transnational exchange, and private sector developments. They have become central to a variety of public and private infrastructures. Often, biometric technologies and data are not built from scratch, rather they are reformulated and repurposed to fit new times, places, and contexts. Automated face and fingerprint identification on smartphones, and biometric data in ID cards, are underwritten by similar methods of body measurement developed by 19th and 20th century eugenics, anthropology, statistics, and criminology researchers. States have appropriated biometric databases as digital platforms, which often serve as foundations upon which other infrastructures are organized. Biometric systems have been used, and reused, for purposes ranging from the delivery of government services to policing, from tracking refugees to COVID-19 mitigation efforts. This open track invites submissions that address the movement of biometric practices, and their social consequences. Panelists will explore not only how biometric techniques constitute emerging forms of identity governance, but also how they move across time and place, reorganize existing practices, and produce new kinds of infrastructures. Even in new contexts, biometric systems carry the biases and intentions of prior ones. These systems can fail, and present asymmetrical benefits and harms that reinforce inequalities related to race, gender, class, age, and disability. These systems also shape the lived experiences of citizenship,

migration, surveillance, and access to services. This panel welcomes papers that leverage STS concepts and methods to probe the trajectories, implementations, and implications of biometrics on the move.

Participants:

Measuring All Parts: From Colonial Classification To Contemporary Biometrics *Gayas Eapen, North Carolina State University*

The scientific process of racialization, predominantly in the 19th century, rendered man-- the composite of mind and body- into a thing. According to Denise Ferreira da Silva (2007), processes of measurement, counting and classification were part of the “strategies of particularization” wherein the human body got tied to global regions as well as mental ability. These processes of scientific abstraction and classification can also be traced to the beginnings of biometric fingerprinting as well as taxonomic photography (Sengupta, 2003; Pinney, 2014; Breckenridge, 2014). This presentation will attempt to develop a more comprehensive understanding of the processes of scientific abstraction that started in the 19th century for governing populations, both in the colonies as well as the metropole. This would form the first site of analyzing biometrics. Using this, I will gather how contemporary use of biometric technologies both map on to the lineage of colonial use, but also echo similar anxieties from those who resist them. I would use instances of disciplined mobilities in north India that deploy biometrics for this analysis. This would include examples of rampant use of facial recognition, fingerprint- and iris-recognition, but also more extended use of biometrics for authenticating services, such as RFID tags to access highways, entering public transportation or receiving welfare or healthcare services.

Quantifying the “National Physique”: Deterioration, Degeneracy, and the British National Anthropometric Survey, 1904 *Michelle Spektor, Massachusetts Institute of Technology*

In 1903, the United Kingdom’s War Office announced that up to 60 percent of men who presented for military enlistment were physically unfit for service. Amid growing fears about national decline, the government convened an Inter-departmental Committee on Physical Deterioration to investigate the issue. After consulting anthropologists from the British Association for the Advancement of Science (BAAS), the Committee’s 1904 Report recommended a National Anthropometric Survey – a large-scale collection and investigation of biometric measurements of British citizens’ bodies – to determine the occurrence of physical deterioration in the population. Relying on archival materials about the BAAS Anthropology Section and the Inter-departmental Committee, the presentation shows how the Survey emerged as a solution for these goals and why it was never implemented. It examines how its design was shaped by (i) the Inter-departmental Committee, who hoped to measure the population’s health and develop social reforms, and (ii) BAAS anthropologists who wished to advance their eugenic research on racial classification in the UK and promote anti-immigration policies. In the process, these groups imbued the Survey’s methods with varying, and at times conflicting, understandings of national identity. Drawing on STS and related scholarship on biometrics, the paper presents the Survey as a precursor of contemporary state biometric infrastructures that demonstrates how systems that encompass entire citizenries still contain politics of inclusion and exclusion. The Survey linked measurements of citizens’ bodies with notions of national belonging, and reflected tensions over industrialization, class, urbanization, immigration, race, and empire – dynamics that resonate in national biometric systems today.

Populational Thinking in the Development of Fingerprinting Knowledge: The Case of China’s Fingerprint Investigation Commission *Daniel Asen, Rutgers University - Newark*

In 1936 the Nationalist government of China convened a Fingerprint Investigation Commission and tasked it with developing a new system for indexing fingerprint cards in Chinese police agencies and prisons. The Commission's first step was to survey the "racial" distribution of fingerprint characteristics within China's population, which it did by engaging with academic research in physical anthropology and dermatoglyphics. While the Commission's work was short-lived and ended ambivalently, police and forensic experts in China would continue to research fingerprint patterning at the level of populations throughout the rest of the 20th century, as would officials and researchers in other countries. This paper examines why police and judicial officials in China and elsewhere pursued research into population-level variation in fingerprint patterning and what this area of juridico-scientific knowledge can tell us about the ecologies of knowledge and expertise in which modern fingerprinting developed. The paper's argument is that the epistemic authority and practical competencies of law enforcement officials and academic researchers were not clearly differentiated in populational research on fingerprints, which incorporated basic practices of police and judicial record-keeping as much as it relied upon analytical concepts and data-sets drawn from published research in the sciences. Given the work being done today to improve the scientific validity of fingerprint evidence, it is notable that this older area of fingerprinting knowledge was also one in which officials strove to incorporate scientific knowledge into identification work, even if the sources and politics of that knowledge are very different than they are today.

Session Organizer:

Michelle Spektor, Massachusetts Institute of Technology

Chair:

Ranjit Pal Singh, Data & Society Research Institute

501. Making Science in Public I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

Participants:

Activism Otherwise: At the Limits of Relation and Description in Genomic Medicine *Kristin Bright, Middlebury College; University of Toronto*

What happens to social health movements when medicine is repositioned around a genetic pathway or protein? This paper examines the implications of precision medicine for how activists communicate about lethal diseases like cancer, HIV, Alzheimer's, and rare disorders. Biogenetic therapies pose a challenge to existing forms of patient advocacy. Such movements tend to see patients of a particular disease as a group and model their activism and energy on movements similarly oriented around groups (e.g., BIPOC, LGBTQ+, feminist movements). Patient activism has taken a number of public forms, from congressional lobbies to media campaigns. But with the development of gene-targeted therapies, the idea of a disease as organ-centered is changing. What are the implications for activist relation and communication? In conversation with feminist/queer phenomenology and new materialisms (Barad 2003, Bennett 2010, Puig de la Bellacasa 2011, Chen 2013), this paper considers activist practices and artifacts at the edges of where they were and are becoming, e.g., in the cattails between proteins, persons, impressions, markers, social networks, and data science. Drawing on ethnographic research with patient activists in Canada and the US, I consider how activists use stories to make otherwise abstract mutations, molecules, and numbers visible—yielding a kind of activism otherwise, at the borders of public science and description.

Atheist and non-religious publics' engagement with media representations of science: science as 'cultural identity'? *Will Mason-Wilkes, University of Birmingham*

In popular discourse and media representations, (e.g. Dawkins 2006) science and atheism are often presented as fundamentally aligned. Some recent research has focused on the relationship between scientists and atheism or non-belief, with Ecklund et al. (2019) providing a comprehensive global overview of professional scientists' beliefs regarding, and attitudes towards, (non)religion. At the same time, recent research (e.g. Jones et al. 2020) has called for a shift away from research which focuses on public perceptions of or attitudes towards science, to a focus on how publics identify with science, or how 'science' can act as (an aspect of) a distinct cultural identity. In line with these new directions in research, this paper presents data from a pilot qualitative study with atheist and non-religious publics in the UK. Specifically, the project aimed to uncover the ways in which atheist and non-religious individuals engaged with specific media representations of science, understood these representations in relation to their atheism or non-belief and factored these representations into their atheist or non-religious identities. Unpicking how media representations of science are understood by atheists and non-religious individuals, and factored into atheist and non-religious identities helps us to reconceptualise the relationship between 'science' and 'publics' as distinct and separate entities. Instead, this approach allows us to start to trace the ways in which 'science' (broadly conceived) can act as a central and important cultural resource in Western societies which is drawn upon by diverse publics in diverse ways. References Dawkins, R. 2006. *The God delusion*. London: Bantam Press. Ecklund, E., Johnson, D.R., Vaidyanathan, B., Matthews, K.R.W., Lewis, S.W., Thomson, Jr., R.A. and Di Di. 2019. *Secularity and science: What scientists around the world really think about religion*. Oxford: Oxford University Press. Jones, S. H., Elsdon-Baker, F., Catto, R., & Kaden, T. 2020. "What science means to me: Understanding personal identification with (evolutionary) science using the sociology of (non)religion". *Public Understanding of Science*, 29(6): 579–596. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662520923110>

Atmospheres of mobilisation: attending to the affective qualities of science- and technology-related patient activism *Lisa Lindén, Department of Sociology and Work Science, University of Gothenburg*

This presentation focuses relations of publics and scientific knowledge within the context of patient activism. Drawing upon ethnographic fieldwork with a gynaecological cancer patient organisation in Sweden, I discuss how patient activists mobilise, contest and negotiate biomedical knowledge to enact gynaecological cancer as an issue in need of scientific and public attention. I relate to the STS agenda around "evidence-based activism" (Rabeharisoa et al. 2014) and "research in the wild" (Callon and Rabeharisoa 2003) that emphasises STS research around patient activism as a study of (the assembling and mobilisation of) public concerns. While being immensely helpful in attending to patient activists' production and mobilisation of knowledge, it does not emphasise the affective dimensions of such practices (as discussed in Lindén 2020). Utilizing the notion of "affective atmospheres" (Anderson 2009) I discuss the performative effects of, often fleeting and elusive, affective qualities of activists' engagement with science and technology. Doing so, I argue that the notion of affective atmospheres might help STS researchers in describing aspects of science- and technology-related activism easily overlooked when conceptualised as primarily epistemic and material matters. Anderson, B. (2009). Affective atmospheres. *Emotion, space and society*, 2(2), 77-81. Callon, M. & Rabeharisoa, V. (2003). Research "in the wild" and the shaping of new social identities. *Technology in society*, 25(2), 193-204. Lindén, L. (2020). Moving evidence: Patients' groups, biomedical Research, and affects. *Science, Technology, & Human Values*, 0162243920948126. Rabeharisoa et al. (2014). Evidence-based activism: Patients', users' and activists' groups in knowledge

society. *BioSocieties*, 9(2), 111-128.

Democratic Science and Symbolic Violence : A Relational Approach to Experts and the Public *June Jeon, Chungnam National University*

How scientific experts are classified from the public? Science and Technology Studies (STS) scholars have shown jurisdictional and network strategies of experts that prohibit the democratic practice of technoscience and have developed various social platforms for the public engagement of science. Despite various institutionalized practices for the public engagement of science, scholars have continued critical appraisals on how these alternative platforms can resolve social inequality, mediated by science and technology. In this context, this paper highlights the boundary-work between experts and the public with the theoretical lens of symbolic violence. In 2017, I conducted a laboratory ethnography at a bioenergy research center, located in the Midwest, United States. I participated in public events by the center and conducted follow-up interviews with participants. Experts and public members discover each other's habitus during the interaction, and they classify each other. This relational boundary-work becomes a foundational mechanism for symbolic violence that urges the public to define their 'publicness.' The public internalizes the attitude of indifference—a practical logic of 'rational citizens' who do not engage with scientific debates—that orchestrates massive disengagement of the public from the stage of science. Therefore, experts classify and structure the public as a subject of symbolic violence. This paper reveals some controversies around bioenergy technology, and most of all, contributes to an understanding of social forces that marginalizes the public by manufacturing their voluntary silences.

Science and Emotions: Staging Stories from Science for the Publics *Kaya Akyüz, University of Vienna*

In February 1978, at a meeting of the American Association for the Advancement of Science, a pitcher of water was poured on Edward O. Wilson by demonstrators as he was preparing to hold his presentation. With this moment being told repeatedly by numerous actors including the main character, Wilson has been transformed into a prophet or martyr of science as well as becoming possibly the most well-known sociobiologist. In this paper, I follow how this episode appeared in different forms and formats of science popularization over the years, from biographic material to documentaries, popular science books to book reviews. In doing so, I am focusing on both how science is communicated through emotions and how this case contributes to the (re)production of a specific version of biology of the social and its history. With the analysis of the performative aspects of the story, I highlight how a scientific controversy is brought to diverse publics with the demonstrators' attack as one of the main frames of reference. While this paper is based on a very specific episode from a well-studied controversy, it contributes to the STS literature on science communication by bringing emotions to the center and exploring their role in staging stories from science for diverse publics.

Session Organizer:

Sarah R Davies, University of Vienna

Chair:

Sarah R Davies, University of Vienna

502. Innovation, STS and Good Relations: Building Socio-technical Futures in Unequal and Uncertain Worlds - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Innovation is a central element within public and private discussions over the form and direction of socio-technical change. However, 'innovation' as a topic presents STS scholars with a number of closely-related dilemmas. Is our role to deconstruct and challenge the very idea of innovation or else to seek ways of augmenting and developing it in a more socially-engaged and responsible fashion? Should we view innovation as a source of social and

environmental challenges or else as a positive means of addressing those same challenges? Given the fast-expanding literature within Innovation Studies in particular, should STS scholars seek to build intellectual bridges with neighbouring disciplines or else develop more distinctive theoretical and empirical perspectives? Faced with uncertain and unequal worlds, is innovation – and innovation scholarship – part of the problem or the solution? In this session, we invite contributions from STS scholars whose work addresses the interface between innovation, STS and 'good relations': including global issues of inequality and uncertainty. We welcome empirical studies exploring innovation in specific contexts but also those which seek new conceptual possibilities regarding STS and innovation. What is – and what should be – the relationship between STS scholarship, innovation and the building of stronger social and environmental relations? And what does this mean for the future governance and practice of innovation? Potential topics include: Innovation, futures, governance, challenges, uncertainty

Participants:

Challenging the Normalization of Organizational Innovation:

The 'Innovation Script' as Analytic and Interventive Device.
Judith Igelsboeck, Johannes Kepler University Linz

Innovation keeps presenting itself as one of the most desirable and pervasive contemporary ideologies. As a facet of this collective praising of innovation, proving 'innovative ability' has become an integral part of contemporary organizational life – turning the ways in which organizations innovate into a powerful means for societal change. Even though innovation is interwoven with the paradigms of creativity and originality, the very idea that innovation can and should be 'managed', the dominance of the 'Silicon Valley innovation model', or the widespread uptake of 'Design Thinking' bear witness to strong isomorphic traits and normalization when it comes to handling the pressures and risks posed by innovation. What are the societal consequences, if diverse organizations follow rather similar recipes for being innovative and showing innovativeness? The presented study problematizes these dynamics with the help of the 'device' of the 'innovation script' – prescribing (1) which actors are eligible to partake in innovation activities (innovation ensemble), (2) how the responsibilities are to be distributed between them, and in which (3) atmospheres innovations can be expected to happen (innovation stages). The 'script' (as many other dramaturgical metaphors) derives its analytic qualities from its longstanding refinement in the study of organizational cultures and institutions. The 'script' – as conceptualized in STS – lures us into crossing the boundaries of analysis and intervention by engaging in the activity of 'scripting' respectively 're-scripting'. The participatory theatre-play 'Enacting Innovation' (as performed at the Ars Electronica Festival 2020 <https://ars.electronica.art/keplersgardens/en/enacting-innovation/>) was one experimental attempt of doing so.

Can we expect scientists to be good entrepreneurs? Exploring the innovation-ability of publicly funded research projects *Gisle Solbu, Norwegian University of Science and Technology*

Public research investments are increasingly tied to narratives about innovation. In particular within fields of emerging technologies, like nanotechnology and biotechnology, stories about how innovation will drive deep socio-technical change give legitimacy to spending substantial amounts of public money on new funding schemes. Within these stories the scientists, manifested through the research projects' principal investigators, often figure as the main heroes. They are imagined in policy documents as dedicated, risk-willing and self-sacrificing professionals, not only set out in life to solve grand societal challenges but also striving to translate their research results into prosperous business ventures. In this presentation I ask the question: are we expecting too much? Drawing on a case-study of a publicly funded center for biotechnology research and innovation in Norway, I will discuss empirical examples that

show tensions between policy ideas about innovation which are largely based on an imagination of an entrepreneurial-minded scientist and the restrictive conditions for engaging in innovation activities that exist within the daily practices of academic research. I argue that an important role for STS in the study of innovation is to create a link between overarching policy discourses and the mundane practices of R&D, and in this way clarify the situated, multiple and sometimes unpredictable conditions that influence innovation outcomes.

«Innovation», An Ideology That Will Not Make A Better World
! *Jclaude Ruano-borbalan, CNAM (National Art & Craft Conservatory) Paris*

Even if not universal, «innovation» has become, since about half a century, the backbone of the strongest ideology of current times, and surely the more expanded one worldwide, though essentially shared by urban, active, educated, liberal and entrepreneurial world class. Armadas of engineers, managers, civil servants and institutions or firms constantly promote the unique and so-called «best» way to solve problems or enhance development and prosperity. Nowadays even if in a critical way, «innovation» is the key for accessing and being part of debate, actions and mobilisations to face major challenges for «transitions». But Innovation doctrines (from public policies for research and innovation to entrepreneurial University spreading off to promotion of individual creativity all azimuth) is essentially a way to avoid conflicts and political questions. using examples coming from different situations, namely University programs for innovation or promotion of Entrepreneurial universities or innovation in public administrations in United Arab Emirates, China, Belgium, Georgia, Lebanon, France the paper will discuss the ideological framework of the «innovation and creativity/entrepreneurship» narrative. It will propose to consider, despite inevitability of ideology, the possible interest of the long emancipatory tradition and institutions within Education and academia. It will refer to some theoretical Pillars such as Matha Nussbaum's approach of «non profit» education or French critical or analytical theory (Bourdieu, Boudon, Crozier; Ecole des Annales, etc.) and obviously STS approaches of Knowledge, beliefs and its link to material or intellectual technics or organisations.

Responsibility for Epistemic Innovation *Gwen Ottinger, Drexel University*

As a philosophy and approach that aims to synchronize innovation with the needs of society, Responsible Innovation (RI) has remained largely agnostic about what types or domains of innovation ought to be pursued. This paper highlights an important unmet social need for a particular kind of innovation: epistemic innovation, or invention of new concepts for understanding the world, along with the methods and instruments for representing the phenomena that they describe. Epistemic innovation is a little-appreciated but urgently needed corrective to epistemic injustice, which prevents disadvantaged groups from fully communicating their experiences of the world to decision-makers and more privileged publics, and which stands in the way of the good moral relations necessary to overcome social and environmental justice. Epistemic innovation is also necessary to conducting just, inclusive assessments of the effects of new technology, including those developed under the banner of RI. Drawing on examples from the environmental justice movement, I show how epistemic innovation can promote awareness of and action on problems faced by disadvantaged communities in particular; I also show how it can perpetuate an unjust status quo. Responsible epistemic innovation, I argue, requires close collaboration between disadvantaged groups and those who enjoy the resources and authority of scientific institutions. It should be seen as a professional obligation of scientists and technologists, and included as an explicit goal of RI, in order to repair moral relations between science, politics, and marginalized communities and thus promote just futures.

Towards a Map of Multiple Roads: Situating the Future of Co-creation in Europe *Anja Kathrin Ruess, Munich Center for Technology in Society, Technical University of Munich; Ruth Müller, MCTS TU München*

Over the last 40 years, technology roadmaps have emerged as allegedly useful tools for linking the results of research and innovation to the specific frame of policymaking. At the same time, STS research has critically emphasized the performativity of roadmaps as well as their limited capacity to reflect complexity and uncertainty. In this paper, we examine the roadmap as a tool of both policymaking and science communication by drawing on our own experience in creating – and rethinking – a policy roadmap. As part of the EU Horizon 2020 research initiative SCALINGS (2018-2021), we have conducted research about co-creative innovation practice across countries, instruments and technological domains, with the explicit aim of creating a policy roadmap for co-creation in Europe. To overcome the tension between the expectation to provide concise policy recommendations and the ambition to take into account the socio-cultural particularities of our empirical cases and foreground issues of social justice, diversity and equity, we propose a novel take on roadmapping. Instead of making one-size-fit-all recommendations, we developed a question-based approach in the form of a Social Impact Assessment that offers multiple roads for different stakeholders in their respective contexts. Taking a reflexive stance towards both our roadmap and our take on roadmapping we hope to sensitize policymakers and co-creation practitioners for more inclusive forms of innovation. We also hope to spark the academic debate about more interventionist STS engagement, e.g. by twisting traditional instruments of technoscience governance.

Taking the Innovation Cure: Futures, Ambivalences, Contextualities, Democracies. *Alan Irwin, Copenhagen Business School*

Innovation is often heralded as the cure for the economic, environmental and social challenges facing the nations and regions of the world. It follows that public policies for research and innovation represent an important means of building – and talking about building – the futures. On the one hand, this draws attention to the distinctive ways in which innovation policies are imagined and performed in different global settings. On the other, there is a remarkable sense of familiarity across contexts as similar concepts and innovation models are proposed. A research project at CBS is currently exploring these isomorphic-difference relations. Given the ubiquity and importance of ‘innovation talk’, it is unsurprising that several fields of scholarship have sought to explore the causes, characteristics and consequences of innovation. Against this background, this paper asks the question: how can – and how should – STS engage with innovation? An answer is sought under four main headings: futures, ambivalences, contextualities and democracies. The conclusion is that STS brings important conceptual and empirical resources to our understanding of the ‘innovation cure’ – but also that this has implications for STS itself. In particular, STS scholars are challenged to engage in new ways with this ambivalent, contextualised and democratically-significant phenomenon. What role for STS can be imagined in terms of re-fashioning, disturbing and even augmenting the notion of ‘innovation’ itself – and what would this mean for STS’ relationship with neighbouring areas of scholarship?

Session Organizers:

Alan Irwin, Copenhagen Business School
Jane Bjørn Vedel, Copenhagen Business School

Chair:

Jane Bjørn Vedel, Copenhagen Business School

503. Performativity and Pragmatics in Water Governance - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Water governance is one of the critical challenges facing communities, regions, and states around the world in the twenty-first century. Water related crises and inequities, due to their urgency and centrality to existence, call for a pragmatic orientation that can mask the performative nature of pragmatic doing. Science, feminist scholars and queer theorists point out, is both situated and enacted. The idea of performativity, in its many definitions, has been applied across diverse disciplines, including a performative turn in Science and Technology Studies. Recognizing current relations as constructed or performed opens new lines of inquiry into the pragmatics of water governance and water justice. Building on Ballesterero's (2019) insight that technological, material, and legal devices are central to current practices of water governance, as well as to efforts for new forms of governance, we invite papers that engage with the performativity of doing, demonstrating, and/or disciplining (Kirshenblatt-Gimblett 1999) the sociomateriality of the hydrosocial system. What can thinking with performativity contribute to conversations around water justice and water governance? Similarly, in what ways does doing performativity create potential (or not) for enacting different relations of care and/or harm? We are especially interested in bringing together diverse perspectives from scholars, practitioners, activists, and artists. Attending to the practices of water-related (broadly conceived) science and governance, and the ways watery relations exceed these frames, these conversations may consider (but are not limited to): methods, boundaries, relations, flows, effects, materialities, geographies, temporalities, devices, and socio-technical assemblages.

Participants:

Tastings as performance in the anticipatory governance of potable wastewater reuse *Marisa Manheim; Christy Spackman, SFIS - Arizona State University*

Public water tastings have become a common communication strategy for water utilities wishing to bolster public trust in conventional drinking water production (Spackman 2015), and are increasingly being used to advance public acceptance of potable wastewater reuse. In both conventional and potable reuse, utility representatives view tastings primarily as a marketing tool to "overcome" widespread public hesitancy. However, embodied responses have collective power in technological transitions, whether they are performed and co-produced in informal settings, such as homes and offices, or formal settings, such as public water tastings. For example, due to the widespread public disgust for the concept of drinking treated wastewater, few utilities have implemented plans to implement potable reuse. Therefore, we propose that recognizing public tastings as a form of anticipatory governance could expand what participation looks like in these practices. Anticipatory governance aims to capture a more inclusive set of expectations around new and emerging technologies by engaging diverse groups of people, yet the co-produced and performative nature of public participation is often overlooked (Chilvers and Kearnes 2020). Due to the subjectivity of taste, the performativity of public tastings simultaneously surfaces and reconfigures matter and materiality in the co-production of shared definitions of what is "good", a process that destabilizes assumptions of "publics" and "experts". We present preliminary findings from our practice-based, experimental research with municipal water producers in the Phoenix, Arizona region and discuss plans for an upcoming performative public tasting at a local arts festival.

Towards Equitable Groundwater Governance: A Case Study of California's Most Critically Overdrafted Coastal Basin *Michelaina Johnson, University of California, Santa Cruz*

California's Pajaro Valley is a paradoxical landscape, constituting the most critically overdrafted aquifer along the state's coastline while also containing some of the nation's most expensive farmland. As seawater intrusion resulting from over-pumping has decreased the quality of groundwater, the main local water supply, the community has been compelled to

intervene through policy and technical solutions to protect the billion-plus dollar agricultural economy. The Pajaro Valley water agencies' and CA government's technical steps include water recycling, conjunctive management of multiple water systems, and expanded control over groundwater pumping and pricing. The narratives surrounding these projects are performative, claiming these sociotechnical fixes will promote sustainable water use and thus protect the agricultural industry while overlooking the exploitive labor practices and environmental degradation that the current management paradigm sustains. Presently, mostly white technocrats and land-owning farmers control water distribution and management while small-scale growers, farmworkers, low-income residents, and indigenous groups are politically peripheralized. In light of the passage of the 2014 Sustainable Groundwater Management Act (SGMA) in California, which requires stakeholder participation in the drafting of new policies to ameliorate groundwater overdraft, the Pajaro Valley is experimenting with a novel governance structure and management priorities. These reimaginings leave open the degree to which compliance with SGMA will be transformational, particularly for water activists and disempowered stakeholders. My ethnographic research examines whether and how the implementation of SGMA will make groundwater governance and resource distribution more equitable, and the role of historically marginalized groups in catalyzing such change.

The performativity of "sustainable" and "smart" bathing in urban rivers: questioning pragmatic solutions in the Paris region *Gaële Rouillé-Kiello, INRAE / LISIS; Gabrielle Bouleau, INRAE, LISIS*

Paris Region's officials decided that bathing in urban rivers (Seine; Marne) was a key objective for the 2024 Olympic Games. Photomontages of swimming competitions taking place in front of the Eiffel tower have already been circulated. Public authorities promised residents that bathing would be left as a legacy. Building on interviews with the professionals and local stakeholders involved in the "Bathing Plan", this paper examines how the future of (recreational) water is being performed. First, we analyse how bathing has been portrayed as a desirable component of the "smart" and "sustainable" city in the making, through images and discourses, and what are the performative effects of this staging. Secondly, we show that the supposedly pragmatic decisions adopted to achieve bathing within the tight timeframe have favoured capital-intensive and infrastructure-based solutions as well as digital technologies (early warning systems; public app) to monitor health risks in real time. Lastly, we argue that these choices contribute to hinder more integrated modes of water governance and to overlook remaining risks. We state that this tends to reproduce long-standing and intertwined environmental and spatial inequalities, where the city centre is favoured to the detriment of the suburbs. Ultimately, our paper sheds light on the pitfalls of decisions taken in the name of pragmatism for the rapid satisfaction of a (geo)political objective, with little consideration for social imperatives. Adopting a performative approach helps unveil how water governance is not only shaped by expert-knowledge, but also by the "politics of performance" (Hajer 2005).

Transforming Water Governance on the Klamath River: Inserting Cultural Values and Traditional Knowledge Into the Klamath River TMDL Process *Shannan Lenke Stoll*

What might appear to be a purely technical water governance process—the establishment of total maximum daily load (TMDL) clean water standards for a particular river—rests on fundamental assumptions about the value of water. So-called beneficial uses reflect the values of the groups that define them. In California, because tribes were not involved when the State Water Control Board originally identified and defined beneficial uses for rivers, their values were left out of one of the most

important processes governing water resources. Inviting tribal participation in the technical TMDL process after management priorities are defined does not invite meaningful participation. Further, requiring tribes to translate cultural values and traditional knowledge into the technical TMDL narrative can further extend the colonial influence of Western scientific resource management into Native communities. This paper examines how the Karuk Tribe's Department of Natural Resources (DNR) transformed the TMDL process for the Klamath River, making it more inclusive of cultural values and traditional knowledge. By getting "cultural" (traditional uses) and "fish" (subsistence fishing) inserted into the TMDL process as beneficial uses, the Karuk DNR navigated the tension between participation and colonization, facilitating the recognition of Karuk cultural values and traditional knowledge in this water governance process. This was accomplished through the testimony and documentation of the Karuk management perspective by expert cultural translators.

Session Organizers:

Kallista Bley, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Marisa Manheim

Christy Spackman, SFIS - Arizona State University

Chair:

Christy Spackman, SFIS - Arizona State University

Discussant:

Andrea Ballester, University of Southern California

504. The Biomedicalization of Social Medicine? - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Abstract Edit Abstract Biomedicalization scholars have argued that studies of biomedicalization need to be situated in their geopolitical context and within that context's history of approaches to health and healing (Clarke et al 2010). Biomedicalization can be absent in some sites, or it can be contested by a diverse set of other approaches to healing (such as non-Western practices of medicine). Yet such contestations within the field of medicine itself have often been overlooked in the literature on biomedicalization. One such field is social medicine, a field concerned with the social determinants of health and the relations of medicine and social justice. In this panel, we trace the blurred and contested boundaries between social medicine and biomedicine. Some practices of social medicine have included at the same time social forms of care and biomedicalized approaches. Other social medicine practices have explicitly challenged biomedicalization processes. At different times and places, proponents of social medicine have argued that it has been too much biomedicine (at the expense of social, political and legal approaches), or that it has been too little of it (HIV treatment in low income countries, access to gender-affirming therapy). Sometimes, biomedicalization processes initially promoted by social medicine in the name of solidarity or health equity, have been transformed into more techno-science-dependent forms of practice, sometimes in stratified forms. In this open panel, we aim to explore diverse empirical examples of interdependencies, interconnectedness and contestations between biomedicine and social medicine in different historical and contemporary sites.

Participants:

A Hospital Beside Itself: On A Local Form Of Social Biomedicine In Post-Franco Spain *Janina Kehr*, *University of Vienna, Department of Social and Cultural Anthropology*

In my paper, I will talk about social biomedicine as seen from an HIV-outpatient ward of a large university hospital in Madrid, which is singular in its kind in Spain. The outpatient ward was set up in the city in 1998 to reach out, through home visits, to marginalized drug users that had become infected with HIV in the late 1980s and early 1990s through sharing heroin syringes. Back then, the cultural liberalization of the country, a final sigh of relief and cry for freedom from Spanish youth after decades of Francoism, was marked by anxious drug use of all kinds. Exceptionally high HIV-rates were one consequence of drug

consumption, aggravated by the absence of public harm and risk reduction strategies. Today, the outpatient clinic still provides medical treatment and social support to poor HIV-patients through a local form of social biomedicine, in which pharmaceutical and personally attuned care co-exist. By conceiving of the out-patient ward as a hospital beside itself, building on Lisa Stevenson, I will focus on the experimental, uncertain and contested ways through which people are kept alive through an anonymous biomedical approach, while also being knowingly cared for as persons that matter. Relying on ethnographic material from six months of fieldwork in the HIV-ward with physicians, nurses, social workers and patients in 2018, I argue that this local form of social biomedicine has taken on a renewed meaning during the 2008 economic crisis and subsequent austerity years in Spain.

Credibility struggles in the drug field: Users organizations, biomedicalization and substitution treatment in Norway, 1990–2010. *Anne Lie; isa dussauge, University of Oslo*

While substitution treatment is today an established part of the therapeutic apparatus for treating opioid dependence, its history has been more of an obstacle course. Norway had up until the 1990s, a largely non-medical approach to drug dependence, and pedagogical and social work approaches dominated. Opioid substitution treatment programs was discussed for the first time in the context of the AIDS epidemic, but was fiercely resisted by many. The first national program with substitution treatment was launched towards the end of the 1990s, but with restrictive inclusion criteria. In 2004, responsibility for treatment of drug dependence was transferred from the social service to the regional health authorities. International historical and STS scholarship have discussed (bio) medicalization and the relationship between the state and/or public health system and users (e.g. Mold 2008, Campbell 2012 and 2020, Vrecco 2010). In this paper, we will argue that user organizations were crucial in the coming into being and shaping of substitution treatment in Norway, from the 1990s to 2010. Through successfully reframing discourses of risk and promoting addiction as a disease, they were instrumental in biomedicalizing the public health field in Norway, while their attempt at promoting social justice was less successful. Drawing on archival research, newspaper articles, gray papers and oral history interviews, this paper historicizes both substitution programs and notions of users involvement, and contributes to ongoing discussions about drug policy reform and the biomedicalization of addiction.

Society as a Medical Toolbox: The Norms of Trans Social Medicine *Ketil Slagstad*

This paper analyses how trans care was enacted as form of social medicine in the 1980s. In this period, a new model of gender-affirming therapy was established for trans patients in Norway, in which psychiatrists, doctors, psychologists and social workers with a special interest and training in social medicine created new diagnostic and therapeutic practices in which the social aspects of medical transitioning took centre stage. In this paper, I draw on archival material, medical records and oral history interviews with former patients, health professionals and activists to demonstrate how specific notions of the society and the social both underpinned and were mobilised by patients and professionals in these medical practices. I unpack the conflicting ideals and goals of this kind of care, balancing between biomedicine and social medicine. In particular, I ask how social medicine, a kind of care with subversive and liberating potential, perhaps became particularly prone to reproducing normative ideas and ideals of bodies, identities and society.

Stratified livability and the techno-medical condition: bringing in infrastructures of life *Ayo Wahlberg, University of Copenhagen*

Chronic conditions "creep up", cascade and proliferate in unequal ways leading to "epidemics of lifestyle disease", comorbidities,

syndemics and resulting polyiatrogenesis that disproportionately affect the lives of people who are already socio-economically disadvantaged and racially discriminated. At the same time, the effective treatment and normalization of chronic conditions like diabetes, HIV, kidney disease or heart disease requires well maintained chronic care infrastructures, yet lack of access to life-maintaining therapy also disproportionately affects those who most need it. In this paper, building on a six year collaborative project that has cartographically charted how ethnographically and historically situated daily lives come to be swayed by (multiple) medical conditions in different parts of the world, I suggest that we need to re-conceptualize the 'social' in 'social medicine' away from determinants and towards "infrastructures of life", thereby expanding our definition of "biomedical technologies" to include housing, working conditions, sanitation, food, water and air.

Session Organizers:

Anne Lie

Jeremy A Greene, Johns Hopkins University

Chair:

Nils Kessel, Université de Strasbourg

Discussant:

Nancy D. Campbell, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

505. Post-Capitalist Techno-Science II: Some Immanent Critiques

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Under the capitalist mode of production, the world has been brought to a point of profound crisis. The present and previous centers of global empire, the U.S. and U.K., have among the highest mortality rates from the COVID-19 pandemic, while the “K-shaped recovery” exposes the profound decoupling of the pursuit of capital accumulation from that of human welfare. Unchecked global warming threatens civilization itself while rapid ecological declines lead scientists to declare nature “under siege” (Wagner et. al. 2021). Uncritical deference to market epistemologies, combined with the industrial-scale manufacture of doubt, has resulted in crises of reproducibility and public trust in scientific findings. Meanwhile, the techno-scientific solutions power proposes point less towards a sustainable capitalism than towards increasingly baroque regimes of rentiership. Critical energies within Science and Technology Studies have often been directed against the unexamined assumptions and externalities of techno-science per se rather than the concretely-existing problems of techno-scientific capitalism. Acknowledging and aiming beyond this problematic, this two-part panel takes up the urgent agenda of a post-capitalist techno-science, asking how such a project has been approached in the past and could be accomplished in the future. Bringing STS scholarship into critical theoretical and historiographic engagement with Marxism and other forms of anti-capitalist praxis, panelists will explore the problems and possibilities of scientific and technological work beyond the law of value.

Participants:

The Rise and Fall of Critical Distance: Critique of Science and Critical Science *Evan Buswell*

While the modern period begins with a new science that is at the same time a new philosophy, during the course of the 18th-20th centuries a separation of concerns between science and philosophy is produced both in theory and in practice. In STS, we use this separation of concerns to create critical distance from science, perceiving what scientific practices miss on their own. But this critical distance is nevertheless a historical, limiting construction. In this paper, I will briefly draw out the history of this construction, focusing particularly on the crusade against metaphysics by the Vienna Circle and others. Then, drawing on case studies of my own work in humanities labs, I will argue that we are approaching a historical juncture where critical distance is both no longer what is needed, and no longer what is produced.

(Before and After) Science and Secularism *Spencer Adams*,

University of California at Berkeley

20th-century social theorists from Weber to the Frankfurt School and Sohn-Rethel have critiqued the abstraction, alienation, and worldly disenchantment inherent to modern science and technology, thereby reinforcing characterizations of techno-science's presumed secularism. From the work of Fanon to that of more recent thinkers such as Nasser Zakariya and Stefania Pandolfo, however, forms of worldly engagement irreducible to the secular have been identified within certain kinds of “modern” medical practices and modes of techno-scientific storytelling. Following the lead of this latter set of thinkers, I ask what it would look like to think immanently within and beyond techno-science and its secular characterizations, taking that question as a crucial one for thinking not just about a ‘post-secular’ but also a ‘post-capitalist’ techno-science. Positing that secularism is not epistemologically intrinsic to techno-scientific activity but rather an effect of its real subsumption under capitalist value-relations, I begin by putting into conversation “pre-classical” epistemic virtues, research into the ways scientists engage with climate and ecological modeling tools, and the speculative image that Kim Stanley Robinson gives of post-revolutionary techno-scientific practice in the third installment of his Mars Trilogy. In doing so, I highlight oft-ignored patterns of techno-scientific ritual, habit, and affective relationality that can exceed and thus be diverted beyond value-generation and its secularizing effects.

Reification of Persons and (Per)sonification of Microbes:

Towards a Decommodified Microbiome *Owen Marshall*

For over a decade we have been told that our microbiomes can speak. The germs in our guts “talk” to our brains. Through the mechanism of “quorum sensing” (previously known through the non-verbal metaphor of “auto-induction”) microbes confer with each other in particular “languages”, sometimes resulting in “cross-talk”. The foremost spokesperson for this speech, Princeton molecular biologist Bonnie Bassler, also speaks for corporate shareholders, serving on the boards of directors for multiple pharmaceutical companies, each of which is eager to profit off of the therapeutic affordances of these multispecies conversations. Art-science collaborations and public outreach campaigns have taken note, with various musical or sound art “sonifications” of microbiome data producing literalizations of microbial speech. Reading these phenomena in Marxian terms, as reifications of social relations between living persons and personifications of resulting microbial commodities, I attempt to reverse-engineer the commodified microbiome in an effort to imagine a microbial ecology decolonized by the value-form. In doing so, I reflect on my own work sonifying microbiome data with performance artist Margaret Laurena Kemp, whose critical explorations of racialized embodiment point out the tacitly extractive dimensions of a capitalized microbial ecology, particularly the fetishization of non-white or indigenous microbiological flora as sources of new products.

Session Organizer:

Owen Marshall

Discussant:

Kavita Philip, University of British Columbia

506. Infrastructuring Research: (Re)assembling Collaboration and Place-Making Practices II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

Research infrastructures (RIs) are typically understood as – either centralized or distributed - material, organizational and regulatory formations that aim to facilitate scientific practice in specific domains. While often treated as relatively durable and invisible underpinnings of technoscientific endeavours, the importance of RIs in facilitating large-scale scientific initiatives have recently become increasingly prominent. This panel addresses how the ‘infrastructuring’ of research – i.e. the planning, construction, operation, and maintenance of RIs – provides a key

site for studying how collaboration and particular understandings of place (in relation to e.g. identity) are assembled. We consider infrastructuring processes not only in terms of the sociomaterial formation of infrastructures, but explicitly include symbolic and narrative processes that contribute to the solidity – as well as transformations - of RIs across space and time. Across the sessions, we ask: Which kinds of research activities are included and excluded from infrastructuring processes? How do political and economic dimensions of (especially cross-national) collaboration feature in infrastructuring? What are the implications of infrastructure for how research is practiced, funded, and evaluated? How is the location (or distribution across locations) of RIs perceived in relation to the character of scientific work? How do spatial boundaries of RIs relate to imaginations of their social, political, and cultural ‘location’? Which kinds of identities are formed, transformed, or rejected through the formation of RIs? Which narratives are mobilized to make infrastructures and collaboration work, and conversely, how are these narratives shaped by prior histories of infrastructuring and collaborating?

Participants:

‘Infrastructuring’ exchange of high quality data in BBMRI-ERIC: mapping a contested landscape of access and mobility
Erik Aarden, Alpen-Adria University Klagenfurt

The exchange and widespread use of data has grown into a critical value for biomedical research over the past two decades. To make data exchange possible, standardization of data formats, quality assurance, and securing the visibility of and access to data – activities often summarized as data curation - have therefore become increasingly important. Various STS scholars have studied data curation practices in an effort to understand how the ‘packaging’ and ‘travel’ of data have changed aspects of scientific practice, such as scientific professions (including the creation of new ones) and the epistemic and other forms of ‘value’ attributed to data. The curation and distribution of data have thus been characterized as complex sociotechnical practices, in which data infrastructures play a critical role for enabling ‘data journeys’. In my contribution, I complement such perspectives by exploring how data infrastructures in biomedical research contain particular visions of the promises data contains. I focus on data curation services provided by the European biobanking network BBMRI-ERIC in the form of its IT infrastructure and work on quality management. I trace how these services form interventions in the creation of visible and mobile high quality data for medical research in Europe, and thereby simultaneously draw a map of a European data ‘landscape’ where data can travel to some places, but not to others. I use this case to argue that “infrastructuring” data exchange builds and reflects particular imaginations of technoscientific identities in Europe.

Corporate involvement in the infrastructuring of European R&I.
Luca Marelli

Ever increasingly since the launch of the Lisbon Agenda at the turn of the millennium, the European Union (EU) has projected its future as tightly interwoven with its ‘power to innovate’ through science and technology. All the while, it has increasingly embarked to lay down the knowledge and material infrastructures for an ever more closely integrated and globally competitive European knowledge economy. Infrastructures for research and innovation (R&I) have thus emerged as prominent sites for probing the enabling role performed by technoscientific systems in materializing normative ideas about Europe and operationalizing them within the fabric of the European polity. In this paper, I will explore the role of powerful corporate actors in the infrastructuring of European R&I, so as to trace the implications posed by the growing involvement of corporate actors in research networks for emerging understandings of ‘Europe’. Focusing on the revealing case study of the Innovative Medicine Initiative (IMI) – the largest Public-Private Partnership in the life sciences worldwide – I show how the vision underpinning the governance set up of IMI has been geared towards a redefinition of the public-private boundary within the

European biopharmaceutical research, and a skewed redistribution of agency among the academic and industrial actors involved in the PPP. Most notably, I trace how the initiative programmatically endows “European pharmaceutical corporations” – itself a legitimacy framing – with the capacity to set the research agenda and the epistemic standards of this newly crafted, integrated public-private research and innovation space at EU level. In conclusion, I contend that the striving for competitiveness that is enshrined in the construction of the European health bioeconomy entails tensions and trade-offs with ideals of public accountability, fair distribution of resources, and science as a public good—thus raising salient issues for the ongoing construction of a European identity.

Understanding “fair returns” in European research: Configuring justice, scientific standing, and economic competition in the European space sector through the geo-return principle
Zinaida Vasilyeva, MCTS, TU München

The geo-return principle, also known as “fair return” or “juste retour,” is a main industrial policy adopted by the European Space Agency (ESA) in the middle of the 1970s and applied up until now with little modifications. The principle holds that, in ESA collaborations, a country’s share in the weighted value of contracts must approximate its share of financial contributions over a period of time. As a legal mechanism, geo-return makes the exchange of material resources and expertise between the ESA member-states explicit, predictable, calculable, and “fair”, for it guarantees the proportional return of funds, paid annually to the Agency, back to the countries. The different names of the policy point at two fundamental aspects of the ESA constitution: 1) its recognition of the geographical diversity and national organization in Europe, accompanied by an implicit sense of different scientific and technical capabilities of member states; and 2) its commitment to the moral principle of “fairness” or “justice” as a foundation for an imagined Europe, incorporated in the exchanges between the European countries. In this paper, I approach the geo-return principle from a co-productionist perspective as an element of a European infrastructure of “fairness”, embedded in multiple policies and bureaucratic mechanisms. Thus, the geo-return principle can be understood as a technical-material expression of a certain vision of “European fairness” rooted in democracy and a consensus about how a heterogeneous polity should be governed. Conversely, it reconfigures conceptions of European justice and democracy around economic reasoning of return and scientific reasoning about capabilities. Focusing on the history of the geo-return policy, I will show how the debates about the geo-return, redefinitions of the policy, and new ways of its application manifest shifts in the meaning of what is a “fair Europe” and how this fairness relates to market mechanisms as an alternative instrument for integrating Europe. I suggest that mutations in the role of the members-states in Europe due to the emergence and reinforcement of the European Union as a supra-national political body contribute to the multiplication of meanings of justice and transform “material infrastructure of fairness” without being visible and accountable enough.

Legitimacy construction through collaborative practices: the case of Laserlab Europe
Oguz Özkan, MCTS Technical University Munich

In 2000, the European Commission launched the Integrated Infrastructures Initiative (I3) to connect eminent national research facilities under a European umbrella. I3 represented a departure from previous understandings that European research infrastructures are primarily the big-science, transnational labs that individual member states cannot afford. Instead, it emphasized “Europeanness” through a distributed network that grants transnational access to national infrastructures (TNA) and encourages joint research activities between them (JRA). This paper investigates one prominent I3 initiative, Laserlab Europe

(LLE) that combines the national laboratories for high-intensity, short-pulse laser research. We explore how LLE purposefully pursued a liminal strategy in-between infrastructuring and projectification – in effect, created a model of projectification as infrastructuring – that sets it apart from concurrent efforts around the ESFRI roadmap and the Framework Programme, and allowed it to colonize a space between European and national research. We trace how LLE’s strategy evolved over time, from an initial focus on TNA considered the core of infrastructuring spirit towards a current focus on JRAs with promises towards collaboration with industry and socially robust outputs. While the emphasis of TNA is on “inclusiveness” and “solidarity” that grants all researchers in Europe access to the same advanced machinery and homogenizes different levels of scientific development; JRA operates on the diversity and complementarity of the LLE membership basis for the above-mentioned goals. The analysis of LLE sheds new light on how multiple layers of infrastructuring activities have played out in diverging actor constellations and discursive constructions.

Session Organizers:

Nina Klimburg Witjes, Vienna University
Zinaida Vasilyeva, MCTS, TU München
Oguz Özkan, MCTS Technical University Munich
Erik Aarden, Alpen-Adria University Klagenfurt
Kamiel Mobach, University of Vienna
Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies
Sebastian Michael Pfothner, Technical University Munich

Discussants:

Ulrike Felt, University of Vienna, Department of Science and Technology Studies
Sebastian Michael Pfothner, Technical University Munich

507. Soil Sensing: Methods, politics and experience - III: Sensing soils in agriculture

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

Participants:

Affective Farmer-Soil Relations and Regenerative Farming Practices: Creative Methods *Michiel van de Pavert*
Without a microscope many soil organisms are too small to observe. Moreover, in farming systems that best build soil health (for example, agroforestry and no-dig gardening) sensorial engagements with soils remain limited, because soils are largely left undisturbed. To further complicate the focus on soils this study also centralizes affective relations, which are implicit (and potentially even intimate) most of the time. So, in order to evoke affective responses on soil I am advancing art-based methods as well as audiovisual methods to study the affective relations that emerge between farmers and their soil on regenerative farms. These methods are supported by an ethnographic approach, making use of interviews and participant observations. For the art-based methods, I am testing a number of ‘easy-to-organize’ activities that are designed to encourage participants think creatively about soil. For the audiovisual methods am exploring possibilities for co-creating knowledge through photo/video-voice. Through these methods, I aim to write stories using alternative (speculative) concepts that inspire other farmers for novel engagements with that soil. In this presentation, I will share the methodological design with a view towards capturing experiences with soil sensing based.

(Not) knowing carbon: sensing and measuring carbon in regenerative agriculture and forestry practices *Galina Kallio*, University of Helsinki; *Jenny Rinkinen*, University of Helsinki

Knowing carbon has become an appealing goal in regenerative

agriculture and forestry. The capacity of soil to act as a carbon sink provides a promising domain for climate governance and for taking steps towards the so-called ‘carbon neutral’ future. These aims are not only words in policy and public discourse, but carbon is used to justify and lead sustainability transitions. The challenge is, however, that carbon cycles are invisible to a human eye. In this paper we ask how carbon is known in regenerative agriculture and forestry practices. Through an ongoing ethnographic study of Finnish regenerative agriculture and an interview-based study on continuous cover and protective forestry, we show, first, how carbon is known (measured, visualized, communicated and taught) through scientific knowledge and methods of measurement. Second, we illustrate the multiplicity of farming and forestry practices that indirectly affect carbon sequestration but where the carbon cycle is not actively ‘known’. We show how quantifying and measuring carbon is introduced to the practices of farming and forestry ‘from the outside’, or more specifically from the closely related practices of climate policy, research and market pursuits. At the same time farmers and forest actors are trying to make sense of carbon through their everyday work. We argue that scientific measurements are reducing knowing of and with soils to knowing carbon, leaving aside relevant questions of biodiversity, as well as multiple ways of knowing and sensing tied to localities. We also draw important conclusions of the limits of scalability of carbon knowledge.

Soil Microbiome Capabilities: Re-envisioning Microbial Identity in Agriculture *Marie F Turner*, Colorado State University; *Erika Amethyst Szymanski*, Colorado State University

This presentation re-examines soil microbial identities as emergent capabilities in the move away from green revolution-era synthetic chemistry towards biological agricultural products (e.g., biopesticides, biostimulants). Currently, most biologicals on the market contain single, well-characterized strains of microbes because their functional mechanisms and identities can be easily confirmed. As such, these products fit well into the standard regulatory framework of this-chemical-does-this-thing. The adherence of new products to old regulatory modes is not surprising (Jasanoff, 2004), but is also interesting given that the biologicals market has arisen in part from a new understanding of soils as collaborations of living organisms with emergent properties in spatiotemporally variable communities. In agriculture specifically, these multivariate communities have often been ravaged by chemical and other practices of control (Green, 2020) resulting in poor crop performance and ecosystem decline. While crop performance can be improved with single strain applications, data from agricultural studies show “health” and “productivity” are linked more strongly to diversity of the soil microbiome (Chen et al., 2020). This suggests it may be the not-easily sensed interactions and emergent community capabilities that may be of the most benefit to ecologies, agricultural and otherwise. A shift towards metagenomic and metabolomic technologies may be helping to move away from a this-microbe-does-this way of thinking inherited from the recent chemical history of agriculture and plunge us forward into an era of searching for functional patterns in diverse systems in which we are not always readily able to say exactly whom is doing what.

Soil Regeneration and the Cultivation of Moral Ecologies in Singapore *Vanessa Koh*, Yale University

Moving away from conventional state valuations of land that measure productivity in terms of export crop production and real estate, this paper asks: What does it mean to make time for soil (Puig de la Bellacasa 2015) and to produce knowledge of and on the ground? Through ethnographic fieldwork with urban farmers, I tell the stories of soil companions who are working on regenerating Singapore’s urbanized and disturbed soil and sequestering carbon for the purposes of mitigating climate

change. Exemplified through their regenerative farming methods, my soil companions hew to the beliefs that chemical fertilisers cannot replace nature and that humans must offer something in return to the soil. Sensing the soil, then, becomes a practice through which moral ecologies emerge as people grapple with what it means to live a grounded life. Under this framework, the value embedded within the ground shifts from that of a commodity (cf. Li 2014; Polanyi 2001) to a moral landscape entangled with global anxieties over anthropogenic climate change. Soil regeneration, however, cannot be seen as a cosmology that only acts in opposition to state power. I situate the cultivation of these moral-environmental subjectivities (cf. Agrawal 2005) within the ever-pervasive discourse of land scarcity in the city-state to tease out the moments of tension in which regenerative farming methods are subject to the state's economic valuations of land.

Soil sensing on Radio Sutatenza: an analysis of the archive of agricultural primers *Nicolás Gaitán-Albarracín*

Radio Sutatenza was an initiative focused on promoting a non-formal education through radio schools for the peasant population of Colombia, this kept great importance between 1954 and 1978. This text is an archival investigation on the ways of built and unbuilt soils reproduced in the technical primers supported by this initiative, with particular emphasis on those associated with agricultural activities. Recommended practices to perceive what is a "good or a bad soil" will be particularly explored. The analysis will focus on looking at the translations, the silences, the partial connections, the disconnections and the contradictions which are part of this multiple body that is the soil, written and promoted in the archive.

Session Organizer:

Sebastian Ureta, Universidad Alberto Hurtado

Chair:

Daniel Walls, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

Discussant:

Abby Kinchy, Rensselaer Polytechnic Institute

508. Total Institutions: Technosciences of Care and Control III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Erving Goffman (1961) called both prisons and psychiatric wards "total institutions," gesturing to the intertwined nature of care, capture, and control in efforts to manage deviance of the soul, psyche, or self. This panel investigates institutions and techniques of mental health care in the Global North, South, and colonial contexts, grappling with the criminological, forensic, pastoral and penal impulses of the psy-disciplines. Building from the work of feminist science and technology studies, abolitionist scholarship (Wang 2018), studies of racial capitalism (Robinson 1983), and historical and sociological studies of psychiatry, social services, and the prison industrial complex (Roberts 2001, Metz 2010, Ryan Hatch 2019, Raz 2020, Smith 2020), panelists will explore the connective tissue between the prison and the asylum, probing the practices, histories, expertise and apparatuses within the mental health care professions and other social services (from psychiatry, psychology, psychotherapy, and beyond) that knit together the carceral with the biomedical.

Participants:

Art of Crowd Control: The Psychic Life of the Masses in Computer Vision *Peggy Lee*, Emory University

In the era of Black Lives Matter, crowds of protestors, whether viewed from above or below, have formed a new "surface" for computer vision AI. There is little transparency on police theoretical knowledge of crowds and applied practice, and yet, the unprecedented state imaging and digitization of the crowd continues to mount, producing a unique set of questions and "algorithmic anxieties" distinct in this new perception of "crowd" at the intersections of crowd psychology, art, technology, and

policing. This paper examines the coupling of crowd analytics research with protest surveillance which has inaugurated the imaging of the "masses" with new algorithmic detections: from predicting a protest's tendencies towards violence to identifying deviant political affiliation. The promise of crowd analytics lies in scale, presumably exceeding human vision by containing the crowd into manageable algorithms. However, I argue crowd analytics research as it currently trends replicate a long-critiqued classic urban theory that essentializes and racializes crowd as unconstrained and dangerous, one shared by the contentious history of urban policing. I conclude with a reading of the Bell Labs artistic collaboration by media artist Sougwen Chung and video analytics researcher, Larry O'Gorman to consider the "ethico-political" potential of crowd analytics algorithms (Amoore 2020). Their collaboration explores the computer vision of crowds through the potential of expressivity and emotionality, rather than racist pathology and policing.

Care as (re)Capture: Penal Technologies of Control Amid the Pandemic *Chelsea M Barabas*, Massachusetts Institute for Technology (MIT)

How are data-driven technologies used to expand and reassert the legitimacy of the carceral state during moments of crisis? This paper examines the capacity for technologies of care to uphold certain "fundamental fantasies" (Zulaika 2018) regarding the role of incarceration, surveillance, and social control in maintaining public safety. As Gilmore (2007) argues, a central challenge for social movements is to avoid transitions in regimes of racist policing and incarceration that drive formal but not transformative change. This paper examines how three socio-technical interventions were used during the COVID-19 pandemic in response to widespread calls to significantly reduce the number of people incarcerated in U.S. prisons and jails. While these interventions were frequently couched in a language of humanist compassion and care in the face of a deadly pandemic, they ultimately served to expand the carceral state's capacity to surveil, capture, and control criminalized populations. For example, I analyze how Verus, a voice transcription service that was initially marketed as a suicide prevention tool, is now being used to re-cast incarcerated people as the real threat during the pandemic. Government officials used the pandemic to introduce and expand the use of technologies like Verus to perpetuate a "politics of pity" (Murakawa 2014) by shifting attention away from systematic abandonment and structural violence onto an ethics of personal responsibility and pathologized risk. I illustrate how government officials were able to renovate and reinscribe as critical the death-dealing activities of the carceral state amid mounting pressure to decarcerate prisons and jails.

Digital Shackles: Spatiotemporal Containment and Fugitivity *Gil Rothschild Elyassi*, University of California at Berkeley

This paper relies on ethnographic methods to elaborate a conception of supervision in terms of an ongoing, mechanical affixment of a dominant spatiotemporal order over and against multiple ontologies. Focusing on the ankle monitor and GPS tracking devices, the analysis explores the ways by which penal supervision does not singly affect discipline or control over marginalized subjects, but instead contains people amidst bifurcated ontologies, or indeed in between their own reality and a degraded, datafied reality that, despite being partial, strives to position itself as universal. Building on this conception of supervision, the paper proceeds to explore supervision as a continuous accomplishment wherein technologies such as the ankle monitor, or probation officers, must deal with multiplicity and fragmentation that relentlessly threaten to destabilize ontological dominance. To animate this continuous dimension of supervision, the paper foregrounds certain limitations of the ankle monitor, including its finite battery life and its restricted sensory capacity. Against this backdrop, the paper considers how supervising institutions as well as supervised folks come to deal

with and navigate the liminal or fugitive spaces that inevitably open up between the monitor's finite and degraded world and the worlds of those who are made into its objects. Drawing on the analysis, the paper strives to consider how technosciences and a certain dominant imagination (which we may, in short, denote in terms of whiteness) incessantly labor to assemble unstable and oppressive worlds that require ever more resources to maintain.

The Digital Rape Complaint: Allegation Escrow Technology and the Social Dynamics of Rape Reporting *Kelli Moore, New York University*

In the #MeToo era private actors increasingly organize against sexual assault and harassment using information escrow technologies that advance new social dynamics of victim reporting. At private and public entities such as college campuses so-called "allegation escrows" are electronically encrypted applications that provide algorithmic fixes that introduce a crowdsourcing paradigm into sexual assault complaint strategies. These tools transform rape and harassment from the problem of "he said, she said" to "he said, they said." Allegation escrows originate in the distinctive bonds, deeds, and documents of contract law. Users electronically log complaints, which are only released to officials when there is a match among multiple complaints and the same offending individual. Callisto® and JDoe® are designed as sexual assault reporting applications. I use them to consider how these escrow models shape legal evidentiary futures, the social dynamics of rape reporting, and feminist studies of technology by incorporating Value Sensitive Design principles.

Session Organizer:

Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley

Chair:

Beth Semel, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

509. Data (Dis)trust In The Global South: The Case Of Covid-19
- I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

What kinds of data have we produced at the local, national or transnational scale to deal and respond to Covid-19? Over the past year we have grown accustomed to measure, quantify, report, visualize, and account for all aspects of our lives. This has also come with a growing need for "valid" data and what it means to produce, share, circulate, and trust it. The assumption that data, especially more data, will lead to societal betterment is one that tends to pervade both academic conversations in data studies and public discourse. We do not argue against the importance of generating data in the face of local and global problems. Rather, we seek to challenge the assumption that critical analysis of, and intervention into, data infrastructures should happen primarily at the stage of data production. In conversation with citizen science studies the panel argues that data distrust must be taken as an integral part of data infrastructures and capacities—particularly in the context of the global south. This intervention is relevant in that it seeks to destabilize a globally adopted dichotomy that pits people who reject scientific findings against other forms of knowledge. It builds on the contention that data (dis)trust is not a "cultural" attitude of the public, but rather the result of situated processes through which frustration, uncertainty, and cynicism are enacted and produced. We are interested in understanding how data distrust—particularly around health and Covid-19—is produced and mobilized within various and transnational social fields and institutional settings.

Participants:

Trustification and proxy variables in technology discourses "for good" *Garfield Benjamin, Solent University*

Discourses around trust for technologies aimed at a "public good" tend to emphasise the need to get, create or build trust. But this is often framed as a quantifiable process, echoing problems of consentification already prevalent across data and health contexts, exacerbating inequities in benefits and harms suffered by non-white, non-cis-het male, and/or disabled communities

(among others). These problems place a burden on people to trust rather than government or technology organisations to be trustworthy. The quantification of trust in particular introduces problematic assumptions: that trust can be converted into a percentage figure; that there is an acceptable level of trust for public use; that the purpose and aims of this majority trust level constitutes an acceptable and non-exclusive "public good". This paper discusses processes of trustification, taking examples such as contact tracing apps during the Covid-19 pandemic as well as wider public data and public technology initiatives. How does trustification operate? How does it collapse harms, privileges and experiences into a single metric of risk (a single sliding scale of cost-benefit)? What wider contexts does it ignore in terms of existing unevenly distributed levels of access to employment, healthcare, and other privilege-based assumptions of what public "good" is? What historical and systemic inequities and injustices (like racialised medical experimentation or surveillance) are ignored in order to blur forms of distrust? The paper will critically assess trust as a set of minimum requirements and argue that trustification operates through proxy variables that ignore lived experiences and social injustices.

To Trust Or Not To Trust *Laura Herrera, ISUR - UNIVERSITY OF THE ROSARIO; Álvaro Crovo Godoy, ISUR*

From our investigation about the preventive measures for Covid-19 that have been displayed in Colombia, ISUR found that since the beginning of the pandemic there has been a massive share of information about the number of positive Covid-19 cases and the ways to prevent it. Although it seems to be a significant effort from the government to collect and share this information, the contradictions between local and national authorities, the lack of academy and civil society's participation in the production of official data and the greed of protagonism from the national government have produced uncertainty among citizens, which has led to a general feeling of frustration and resignation regarding to the spread of the disease. To reach these observations, ISUR elevated eleven petitions to different EPS (health care institutions) to collect information about the politics that have been implemented to prevent Covid-19. Also, the official information published by the government about the evolution of the pandemic has been analyzed and we began to develop a report about the use of technologies, good practices and future recommendations for the management of information during public-health related emergencies. It is important for private and public health institutions to regain the trust of the population, especially for the short and long-term challenges of the Covid-19 pandemic and future emergencies. STS are the appropriate field to attend this challenge, because a proper strategy for the propagation of scientific information could settle citizens' dilemma to trust or not to trust in official data during emergencies.

The Covid-19 Paradox: Why did Advanced Nations disproportionately report more infections and deaths, and did the United States lead the way? *Richard B Duque, George Washington University*

COVID-19 has accounted for two million deaths worldwide through February 2021. What is paradoxical is that early on in the pandemic this novel virus seemed to target the Advanced Nations of the North disproportionately more than Developing Regions of the South. Yet historically it is less developed regions that suffer as much and often more during pandemics. A cross-national comparison of 163 nations and their COVID-19 experiences, combined with a national focus on the United States case, suggests evidence of both "Technoscience Inequality" and an emerging political "Boundary Object" arguments to explain this paradox.

Healthcare Experiences and the Covid-19 Vaccine *Victoria Siaumau, California Polytechnic State University, San Luis Obispo; Jane L Lehr, California Polytechnic State*

University

Health disparities across individuals with marginalized and racialized identities coupled with historical and present day discrimination results in the mistrust of the US healthcare system. The discourse around the mistrust of this system has recently had a resurgence as the novel Covid-19 vaccine has been introduced to the public. While the Covid-19 pandemic has exacerbated previous health disparities among marginalized peoples (Chowkwanyun, et. al, 2020; Krause, 2021), making these individuals most in need of getting vaccinated, there is reported hesitancy to receive the vaccine within these communities. The goal of this study is to: understand the experiences that marginalized groups have encountered in healthcare settings, how these experiences create or contribute to (mis)trust of medical institutions, and how these experiences intersect with healthcare access and (mis)trust to influence their decision to receive the Covid-19 vaccine. While most current research focuses on race, this study also aims to understand how identities of class, gender identity, sexual orientation, education, and age, in addition to race, intersect with previous experiences of medical discrimination and understanding of historical medical atrocities influence someone's decision to vaccinate or not. This research allows us to better understand how we can design and restructure healthcare programs and institutions to be more trustworthy, accessible to all communities, and legitimized by marginalized peoples.

Session Organizers:

Mayra Alejandra Flores, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

Jorge Nunez, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

Chair:

Sofía Carpio, Kaleidos Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

510. Transnational and Transgenerational STS: Collaborations, Methods and Pedagogies

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

This open panel extends from extensive dialogue about TRANSnational STS at the 2018 annual 4S conference in Sydney, which spawned an array of new collaborations and further conversation. The goal of the panel is to keep the dialogue going and open, taking transnational STS in new directions. Papers will explore structures and dynamics that work against pluralistic knowledge production. Papers will also examine educational programs and research projects designed to counter entrenched geographic, disciplinary and generational hierarchies. Inspired by critical university studies and radical education thinkers like Paulo Freire, Gregory Bateson, and Gayatri Spivak, we hope to help conceptualize and build "good relations" in STS, in keeping with the 2021 4S conference theme. Contributions may address, among others, the following questions: -What pedagogical philosophies (explicitly or implicitly) orient differently situated STS programs, and to what effect? -What tactics do STS programs use to stay tuned to both local and transnational contexts? -What works against knowledge pluralism in STS? What kinds of educational, research and publishing infrastructure is needed to support knowledge pluralism in STS? -How have STS programs and projects actively leveraged diverse intellectual genealogies? How have these programs and projects been proactively anti-imperial? -How have differences in political contexts shaped STS programs and projects? -What methods and infrastructures have supported transnational and transgenerational STS collaborations? How are transnational and transgenerational STS research projects administered and governed? How do they set collaborative agendas and what enables them to sustain over time? -How can transnational STS contribute to STS pedagogy and education program building? -How can transnational STS scaffold local initiatives to engage multiple publics, and decision-makers?

Participants:

Concentricity and eccentricity: Academic trajectories of CTS networks in Chile and Argentina *Nicolás Sanhueza, Sociology Institute, Catholic University of Chile*

This research is a qualitative study that seeks to understand the co-production processes of peripheral CTS networks and academic careers of social scientists in Chile and Argentina. Through a narrative analysis of their careers, we investigate the perceptions of their interests, expectations, and their interplay with their disciplinary fields of interest. The results show the importance of the formation of identities, the construction of shared knowledge, as well as the relevance of interdisciplinary work, in competitive academic contexts that demand efficiency in the production of knowledge, among others.

Publishing in STS: agendas, themes and practices among centers and peripheries. *Pablo Kreimer, CONICET; Noela Invernizzi, Universidade Federal do Parana; Leandro Rodriguez Medina, Universidad de las Americas Puebla; Amilcar Davyt, Universidad de la Republica*

The aim of this presentation is to analyze the structure and dynamics of publication in the STS field, reflexively applying some categories of analysis that we have used to study other fields. To do so, we conducted first a quantitative (bibliometric) methodology to obtain a general map of the origin of the authors in 12 of the most important Journals in the field, for a 10-years period, which expectably confirmed the predominance of Euro-American world, although with some interesting nuances. Then, with interviews with the editors, and analyzing a selection of article summaries, we want to try to establish if there are thematic patterns or systematic practices that differentiate the type of published text according to the regional or institutional origin. Specifically, we ask: Is there any relation between the traditional object of STS (hard sciences in the North) and alternative objects (hard sciences in the South)? When peripheral hard sciences and scientific practices are studies, is it done under the same methodological and theoretical assumptions than in the North or can we perceive alternate ways of conducting STS research in the peripheries? Is there a pattern of specialization specific to each of these contexts (e.g. theoretical vs. empirical works; descriptive vs. explanatory works, etc.)? What influence does the origin of the author, and its object of analysis, have on its reception in mainstream Journals? We intend to advance a critical look at the current transnational opening of STS, in particular through publication practices, one of the fundamental axis of these dynamics.

stsing: Doing STS In, Through And Beyond The German Academic System *Stefan Laser, Siegen University; Paula Marie Helm, University of Tuebingen; Laura Kocksch, Ruhr University Bochum; Ingmar Lippert, IT University of Copenhagen; Julie Sascia Mewes, Ruhr-Universität Bochum; Estrid Sørensen, Ruhr University Bochum*

With this presentation, we introduce the recently constituted association "stsing", which offers scholars a new platform to "do" STS in and through Germany (therefore the wording "stsing"). Specific about this platform is its attempt at creative and open understanding of collaboration on the one hand and critical reflection of national, international, institutional, and intergenerational challenges of STS research on the other. Germany's specific funding and institutional structure is of central importance to stsing. Still, stsing is responding to the internationally integrated practices of STS. It addresses the frictions between local bureaucracies and hierarchies as well as global doings and (self-)understandings of STS. We briefly unfold the (hi)story of stsing: a process of negotiating imaginaries, institutional settings, conflicts and mutual recognition. The challenge is to open spaces and account for the heterogeneous people and disciplines engaged with the ideas, methodologies and politics of STS. stsing experiments with

digital as well as analogue infrastructures of assembly that account for a "bubble-like" structure. It draws on thematic "working groups" and regional "table rounds", engages with digital platforms and explores non-proprietary software options. An experimental form of associat(ing) then faces multiple challenges. We focus on one example: intergenerational matters of the academic system and the distribution of resources. Here, stsing aims for a non-hierarchical setup while reflecting on the institutional architectures that set the terms on which we operate (regarding career steps, thought schools, modes of recognition, etc.).

Telling stories about air pollution and citizen action in Kaohsiung city *Chia-Liang SHIH, National Chengchi University; CHIA-HSUAN HO, National Chengchi University; Tseng-Yung Kao, National Taiwan University*

The petrochemical industry in Taiwan has been developing over 50 years since the 1970's. Today, the petrochemical industry puts the society at risk due to its aging equipment. The related political, economic, social, and legal systems are also outdated and fossilized. However, the vast majority of citizens are unfamiliar with the systemic risks and lack of right understanding. The risks from operating aging facilities, public ignorance about the risks, and the lack of motivation for industry to improve are crucial factors resulting in local residents suffering from environmental pollution. Therefore, our research team creates the "Kaohsiung database" on the platform, "The Asthma Files" (TAF), and tries to construct stories about Kaohsiung's air pollution with compilation of memorabilia, relevant existing documents, pollution information and other data. The purpose is to raise public awareness through understanding of the Kaohsiung pollution stories. At the same time, we hope that Kaohsiung's experience can be exchanged with the international research community on the TAF platform. It will also help us to reflect on the plight and role of stagnant industry and urban governance in Taiwan. We aim to increase international attention and pressure to foster internal perspectives and to improve citizen participation to promote the transformation of Taiwan's enterprises and urban governance.

On the Possibility of Philippine STS: Collaborating toward a Special Issue *Paul Michael Leonardo Atienza, Department of Anthropology, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign; Kathleen Gutierrez, University of California, Santa Cruz*

In the Philippines and for its diaspora, our current political climates demonstrate the urgency with which we must expand concepts of STS. The growth of disinformation networks, authoritarian censorship, neocolonial militarism, and the deliberate extraction of labor through technoscientific industries have demanded that we develop a theoretical framework that attends to the unique historical, political, and social conditions of the archipelago. One of the ways we are working toward this is by assembling current research from scholars who are actively making the field of Philippine STS. For this presentation, we will discuss our guest co-edited special issue on Philippine STS, the first of its kind to be published by the flagship Philippine studies journal, *Philippine Studies: Historical and Ethnographic Viewpoints*. We will cover how the issue and its corresponding papers push the horizon of STS through Philippine empirical data. We will also share our lessons learned, particularly as US-based STS scholars working to question positivist conceptions of science and to bridge intellectual communities transnationally and across disciplines. Yet, still, the special issue features the promise of an open and encouraged intellectual alliance most especially between social scientific scholars and STEM researchers in the Philippines and abroad. Finally, we will problematize the notion of a nation-defined field and instead highlight the ways in which a "Philippine" STS should continue to undo the spatial and temporal limits of the nation form.

Session Organizers:

Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine
Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University
Isha Bhallamudi, University of California, Irvine
Anna Ma, McGill University
Kim Fortun, University of California Irvine

Chair:

Kim Fortun, University of California Irvine

Discussant:

Sharon Traweek, UCLA

511. Ferment as Method: Creating the Conditions for Transformative Relations - I

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Where the 2020 pandemic prompted new desires for hyper-sterile environments, it also sparked interest in the microbe-rich world of fermentation. Home kitchens, wiped clean with bleach and sanitizer, produced effervescent brews, doubling sourdoughs, and funky sauerkrauts. Fermentation provided a collaborative 'contamination' (Tsing 2015) that prompted experimentation, care, and new forms of sustenance amid loss, isolation, and precarity. In fermentation microbes transform their substrates and each other into new forms, textures, flavors, aromas, and matters. Practicing fermentation invites open-ended collaboration across species boundaries; requiring attention (when is it ferment and when is it rot?), care (who needs more water, more food, more salt?), and a willingness for all parties to be changed by the process (no one is coming out the same as they went in) (Fourmier 2020, Maroney 2018, Villalba 2019). Fermentation is more than a material process; ideas, people, and movements ferment. The concept offers a rich metaphor that captures the energy of activists, and transformative potential at any scale. Since ferments can also turn sour, go awry, become toxic, and foment violence and trouble, as a metaphor for responsible change, it contains its own limits. This panel invites participants to ferment as a method in their STS projects. How does thinking with fermentation foreground new configurations of interdependence and care in our work? How might a slower process that allows for unexpected results affect our means of producing knowledge? Might such a method, emergent in the becoming together, open up space to foster 'good' relations or challenge 'bad' ones?

Participants:

'Composting is so Hot'. Fermentation and the Emergence of Low Theories *Elena Beregow, University of the Federal Armed Forces Munich*

This presentation aims at conceptualizing fermentation as "material-semiotic knot" (Haraway) that produces unexpected resonances between the material practices of fermentation and social theory. While fermentation activists such as Sandor Katz generate a practical knowledge of fermentation, in social theory fermentation is often treated as a metaphor for social transformation. A theoretical reading of Katz' position as "low theory" (McKenzie Wark) allows me to sketch out a critical perspective on classical STS approaches of bacterial life such as Bruno Latour's works on the laboratory. I will argue that Katz' low theory of fermentation introduces three theoretical provocations that turn us to the blind spots of a Latourian account of more-than-human life: The role of a) the senses (especially the 'low senses' of smell, taste and touch), b) of ecologies (instead of networks) and c) of the finality of biological life in and through processes of decay and decomposition (instead of endless connectivity). After highlighting the analytical strengths of fermenting as method, in the second part I will consider the risks of such a method by taking a close look at Donna Haraway's figure of 'compost'. The compost figure helps to grapple the multispecies entanglements of ongoingness, but it also is rooted in the populationist project of the 'Chthulucene'. The problematic implications of 'compostism' and its relation to collective fermentation practices will lead me to a suggestion

how 'fermentation as method' could reflexively situate itself beyond an enthusiastic embrace of life on the one and ecopessimism on the other hand.

Fermenting Feminist Pedagogies: Slime Mold Ethics for a Collective Classroom *Regina Yung Lee, University of Washington*

This talk argues that a collective nonhuman-inspired praxis creates possibilities for feminist teaching and learning. I document some of the collective praxes developed over a multiyear implementation of feminist pedagogies in a speculative science studies classroom. Beyond thinking through and with microorganisms such as fungi, yeasts, and symbiotic bacteria, we enact our theories through discussion, modeling, and implementation of slime mold multibeings. Following slime mold capacities for individual and multiple methods of being, and the ways gut flora explode macrofauna-based self-concepts, our course practices and assessment methods are experimental attempts to rethink academic models of rigor along collective lineages. My paper discusses these concepts, outlining some of the assessments and practices in use, and proposes that ferment is a radically queer method for refiguring forms of being in the classroom, rethinking toxic institutional boundaries for transforming how we go on together.

Mycelial Methods: Following Nourishment as Collaborative Pedagogy and Relations *Stephanie Maroney, University of California, Davis*

This presentation from the Hypha Collective centers our experiments in making and teaching inspired by fermentation and fungi. From a mycelial futures storytelling game ala Octavia Butler's Dawn, kombucha-fabric altars for honoring 'mothering' in all its forms, to theatrical reimaginings of radioactive experiments on beagles at UC Davis in the 1950s, this collective is attuned to the queer possibilities that emerge when we slow down and pay attention to process rather than product in our teaching and collaborations. Just as fermentation prompts new ways to "become together," we are inspired by fungus and their mushrooming bodies because they demonstrate models of collaboration, communication, and being that challenge normative human ideas of competition, dominance, and individualism. Fungi shape-shift, consume and become their surroundings, break down nutrients for other beings, and promote interdependence between unlike allies. Our practice is informed by queer and feminist STS frameworks that center relations, practice care, and challenge heteronormative knowledge formations in Western technoscience. In this presentation we give a telling of our activities and invite others to imagine the transformative power of fermentation and mycelium in our pedagogical practices.

Transfermentation: Investigating Trans Experiences Through Fermentation *Sean Nash, Kansas City Art Institute*

For this panel I would like to propose a screening for a new work to be created (or in process) between now and October. In my own experience as an artist and fermentation experimentalist, I have come to connect fermentation with a liberatory sense of becoming, specifically in relation to my trans experience. I have spoken about this connection in a talk titled "Transfermentation: embodied processes of fermentation, art, and trans becoming," for a 2020 Ferment for Food Justice event. In my own rendering, fermentation and trans experience have much in common, and the pace of medical transition can feel parallel to the kind of practiced patience that fermentation also requires. The crock is a cosmic microcosm that can hold the precarity of existence, emotion, and resilience in its small yet enormously interdependent space. I'm curious about the experiences of other trans fermenters and whether fermentation practice as self and community care becomes a personal aid for reflection, a salve, or a symbol of supportive relational networks. For this piece I am proposing to reach out to a network of trans fermenters and

engage in a recorded video conversation about fermentation while we ferment something together. The resulting video document will include audio and video of the conversation, but will be cut with experimental and abstract sound and imagery. Depending on time constraints for the panel, I would present this video or clip as a screening. Some thoughts on format: there may be different creative options for interacting with the screening, or there may be pauses in the video with questions to become interactive and break up spectatorship in the presentation process.

Session Organizer:

Stephanie Maroney, University of California, Davis

Chair:

Xan Sarah Chacko, Wellesley College

512. AI and Feminist STS - III

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Much excellent work has documented how contemporary artificial intelligence (AI) systems reinforce and deepen historical inequalities and oppressions. Further work remains, however, on whether and how AI systems can do otherwise. Recent social movements within AI research have begun to politicize AI technologies and their entanglements with social justice, power relations, and environmentalism (see, for example, #TechWontBuildIt and recent ACM special issues on "AI Activism" and "Green AI"). In a current technology ecosystem dominated by commercial and military interests, however, few possibilities seem to exist for AI practitioners to "strive towards good relations" among humans, technologies, and environments. This panel seeks to investigate how theories, methods, and ways of knowing from decades of feminist STS scholarship can inform the study of AI systems as they are used today. In Alison Adam's (1995) feminist critique of AI epistemology, she emphasizes the need for more concrete examples of a "successor science" based on feminist epistemology and social constructivism to ground AI research. What would "successor AI" look like, built on feminist principles of situated knowledges and standpoint theory? Beyond universalized, depoliticized notions of "ethical AI," might an analysis using feminist STS ground AI systems in complex sociotechnical entanglements and particular histories, geographies, communities, and contexts? This panel features work that engages with these questions and imagines new possibilities for feminist AI technologies. Topics include, but are not limited to, the following: * Social and political movements that aim to centre ethics of care, entanglement, relationality, and responsibility in human-AI systems * Indigenous, Black, feminist, and queer conceptualizations of "artificial intelligence" * Disability studies, feminist STS, and artificial intelligence * Ecofeminism, environmental justice, "green AI" and environmental impacts of AI systems * Standpoint theory and the politics of image, speech, and emotion recognition systems * Intersections and contradictions between feminist health projects and AI in healthcare * New methods and imagined futures for feminist, de-/anti-colonial, anti-military, anti-carceral, anti-capitalist AI Keywords: feminist STS, artificial intelligence, technofeminism, feminist technologies, ethical AI

Participants:

Configuring Ethical AI *Xaroula Kerasidou, Lancaster University*

Ethical AI - in all its benevolent incarnations (Ethical AI, Trustworthy AI, AI for Good, AI for Humanity, etc.) - is part of a mythology that dominates in sectors across Europe and beyond, such as healthcare, policing, security. These are meant to be technologies which do not look, think or act like humans but which, unlike humans, won't get bored or tired of performing narrow, well-defined tasks. Technologies which will "benefit humanity", "free people up to focus on the more human aspects of any job", but only "if we get this right"! Feminist STS have given us the tools to interrogate the recurring myths of Heaven and Hell that accompany digital technologies such as AI, while urging us to pay close attention to their performative powers in (un)making particular worlds and realities. Yet, as I will argue, the stories of super-intelligent machines and "pink-eyed

Terminators” are not the only ones that warrant attention and demystification. In this paper, I will sketch out what I see as an instrumental move away from apocalyptic scenarios of Terminator-style AIs towards figurations of instrumental, efficiency-driven technologies and argue that this, too, is a key part of the new mythology that now surrounds AI. Examining, unpacking and denaturalising the figure of ethical AI as it takes shape in policy debates and documents, I seek to unsettle the well-worn, naturalised tropes which the promises of this “fourth revolution” rely upon, in an effort to open up the possibilities for things to be configured differently.

Memories, Motherhood and Modes of Reproduction in Ugandan Computer Science *Kerry Holden, Queen Mary, University of London; Matthew Harsh, California Polytechnic State University; Ravtosh Bal, Independent Researcher*

In Uganda, the computer science departments at the different universities are occupied by equal numbers of women and men, achieving a balance that is rare in mathematical and engineering sciences. What difference does the presence of more women in computing make to understanding the co-production of technology and society in Uganda or more broadly in Africa? Based on ethnographic research in the computing communities of Ugandan universities, we advance a feminist and decolonial critique of the dominant chrono-politics of globalizing computing. Our analysis progresses along two pathways: first, we focus on how memories of Uganda’s turbulent pasts, scarred by war and poverty, are interpreted in order to frame technoliberal futures in which the present is evacuated. Narratives of past and future are a resource in the chrono-political discourses of both global technology companies and donors and the current political regime, which disguises the symbolic and actual violence of technological interventions and authoritarianism. Secondly, we explore the reproductive role of female computer scientists in their raising children, attending to the needs of communities, working the land and inspiring generations of coders in creating near-futures. This reproductive role is not dialogic to the technoliberal chrono-politics, instead, we argue time syncopates between future imaginaries and everyday life, enabling time to endure in a continuous trajectory as a way to deal with the precarity of globalizing computing. We conclude by arguing that the everyday, near-future is gendered; repaired and tended to by women.

Queering Classifications: How can gender studies’ sustained and radical critique of categorisations and classifications help mitigate unfair bias that arises from AI classification processes? *Eleanor DRAGE, The University of Cambridge*
Categorisations are an integral part of how AI creates rules and identifies patterns or biases, with gender, along with race, age and other ‘soft biometric traits’ often used as data parameters in ML and at other stages of AI development processes. This paper draws on work from critical race, queer, and gender studies, from Judith Butler and Jose Esteban Muñoz to Eve Sedgwick and Gloria Anzaldúa to investigate how this knowledge can help tackle unresolved issues faced by AI practitioners. I focus on two case studies from recruitment, a sector in which AI is increasingly deployed: 1) talent intelligence platforms which attempt to eliminate bias from hiring processes by “stripping” gender qualifiers on the front and back end of the systems; and 2) the “personality profiles” created by AI-video recruiting systems. In doing so, I address the following research questions: If misrepresentation is one of the most pre-eminent sites in the production of racial and gender inequality, should we risk misclassifying an individual’s data by using gender as an input category? Does adding more gender options to input categories translate into a more representative product? If intersectionality states that experiences of gender are produced through interlocking systems of oppression, should gender be a separate

input category from, for example, race? Finally, how are categorisations inflected with Western cultural values? By working against the disciplinary legitimation of rigid categorisation, gender studies can confront the double binds, aporias and logical impasses that halt the progress of debates around categorisations in AI.

Shaping Technology from Care: The case of AI applied to Reproductive Technologies *Natalia Fernández Jimeno, University of Oviedo*

In respect of technology, some feminists authors looked for criteria to determine whether a given technology was feminist or not (i.e. Lane et al 2010), others demanded the inclusion of women in technological designs, and others have developed projects to create feminist technologies (i.e. Schiebinger 2008). All this approaches are necessary, but they are not enough. As we become aware of the malleability of technologies, it is also necessary to care about technologies throughout the life cycle. From a co-production perspective (Jasanoff 2004), they are part of the social fabric, and the context in which they are used cannot be separated from the process of technological development. Technologies as living tools can be shaped by society and their context of living. For that reason there is an opportunity to exercise feminist care in them. The idea of “matters of care” (Bellacasa 2011; 2017) can help us reflect on how things could be different and how it is possible to intervene in the shaping of technology. This will require “to ask ‘how to care’ in each situation” (Puig de la Bellacasa 2011, 100). The aim of this papers is to analyze the case os IA applied to reproductive technologies in order to propose ways in which to intervene from a feminist perspective. The methods include a review of the scientific literature and interviews with embryologists. From this particular case, criteria will be offered to shape this technology. References: Lane, Linda L., Sharra L. Vostral, and Kate Boyer, eds. 2010. *Feminist Technology*. Urbana, Chicago and Springfield: University of Illinois Press. Puig de la Bellacasa, María. 2011. Matters of care in technoscience: Assembling neglected things. *Social Studies of Science* 41(1): 85–106. —. 2017. *Matters of Care. Speculative Ethics in More Than Human Worlds*. Minneapolis and London: University of Minnesota Press. Schiebinger, Londa, ed. .2008. *Gendered innovations in science and engineering*, Stanford: Stanford University Press.

Session Organizer:

Rachel Bergmann, Microsoft Research New England

513. Rethinking Sexuality Amid Pharmacological Sex Therapies II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

Participants:

Direct-to-consumer Telepharmacies and Casual Pharmasex *Ben Curran Wills*

Most sluts, voyeurs, and their interlocutors in the United States who have spent any time on Grindr have seen advertisements for direct-to-consumer (DTC) telepharmacy companies. Nurx, which offers PrEP, STI testing and treatment, and Blue Chew, which sells sildenafil (generic Viagra), are just two of many DTC telepharmacies that target Grindr users. Amongst public health messages and underwear offerings, these ads stand out. Viagra has long been a part of gay sex cultures, but often with a shroud of the illicit. When sildenafil went off patent, companies like hims, Roman and Blue Chew seized the opportunity to market, prescribe, and sell the drug using new models of care provision. Now, instead of purchasing them illegally online or lying to a doctor in person, an interested person can be prescribed and shipped sildenafil in a matter of minutes, all from their phone. This paper explores the argument that when theorizing what pharmaceuticalization means for queer sex, the ease and mechanisms of provision cannot be separated from the drug

experience. Engaging with work in health STS and medical sociology, including (bio)medicalization, this paper explores the implications of what is captured in his recent ad copy, "get hard. It's easy."

"Protecting" Neonatal Vision: Debating the Efficacy and Use of Universal Ocular Protocols *Teresa L Hoard-Jackson, Indiana University - Bloomington*

In the late nineteenth and early twentieth centuries, four German bench scientists and physicians, Carl SF Credé, Albert Neisser, Ludwig Halberstaedter and Stanislaus von Prowazek, conducted research into the microbial causes of gonorrhea and chlamydial infections hoping their discoveries would solve the common problematic occurrence of ocular pathogenic exposure during vaginal birth, which often results in neonatal conjunctivitis, or "pink eye." Soon, these scientists were able to identify the pathogens and develop a prophylactic antibiotic eyedrop protocol to prevent and treat neonatal conjunctivitis. Nearly a century later, most babies born in US hospitals are treated with these eyedrops or ocular ointment regardless of the mother's current sexually transmitted infection status. Due to the advancement of medical technology that allows for rapid STI testing while in labor, medical communities are currently debating about whether the universal protocol should still be in use, what is gained by continuing its practice, and how is health being maintained and constructed through the protocol. My paper surveys several published medical articles to evaluate this debate which leads me to ask the question: how does this post-birth neonatal medical practice help conceptualize Black maternal health – specifically a racialized pregnant woman with a sexually transmitted infection (STI) in this contemporary moment? It is important to consider this conceptual question because of the effects of widely available medical technologies and the framings of pregnant bodies as racialized and gendered sites of contagion which still affect pre- and post-natal care and health outcomes for pregnant folks and neonates today.

Gender and Politics in the Production of Vulnerability in Human Papillomavirus and Cervical Cancer in Mexico *César Torres Cruz, Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios de Género (CIEG). Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México*

The Human Papillomavirus (HPV) currently represents one of the most relevant sexual health problems worldwide, since at least, 80% of sexually active population might acquire it at any time. Prevalence and injuries are more present among women, where this virus might cause cervical cancer. Since three decades ago, several international health organizations as well as countries have adopted a feminist agenda at incorporating gender perspective to pay attention to these and other women's sexual and reproductive health problems. The objective of this presentation is to analyze how sexual politics of feminization of both Human Papillomavirus and cervical cancer are discursively constructed through some political and conceptual uses of the notion of vulnerability in Mexico. Throughout discourse analyses to health attention official documents it is highlighted the conceptual and political uses of gender. I pay attention the ways pharmaceuticals, politics and gender conceptions of vulnerability shape some of the biomedical options within these diseases that reinforce the biomedicalization of women's sexuality. Thus, this presentation will give account on different and complex ways biomedical options intervene sexuality and women's bodies where social and economic uncertainties are present. These political uses of technoscientific options to treat and understand HPV and cervical cancer, reify dominant cultural narratives in relation to female sexuality and risk. These discursive uses of vulnerability that Mexican women are exposed, need wider and intersectional perspectives to avoid the re-victimization of women.

Session Organizer:

César Torres Cruz, Centro de Investigaciones y Estudios de Género (CIEG). Universidad Nacional Autónoma de México

Discussant:

Amaya Perez-Brumer, University of Toronto, Dalla Lana School of Public Health

514. Abolitionist Environmentalism

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

This panel focuses on the intersection between two prevailing logics in contemporary North America: 1) a dominant environmentalism that focuses on harm minimization or optimization of existing industrial systems, rather than the eradication of the root causes of environmental harms, and 2) the carceral infrastructures and technologies that function to surveil, coerce, confine, and punish (Benjamin 2019). We collectively ask what environmentalism can learn from the insights and demands of prison-industrial complex abolitionists. Abolition insists that broad, cross-sectoral transformations of society, and not harm reduction alone, are necessary for alleviating the impacts of carceral violence. We also seek to better understand the possibilities and limits of what environmental research can do for prison abolition, and what sort of broad coalitions might be necessary to avoid the pitfalls of forensics alone. Our collective papers span the gamut of abolitionist thought and praxis, including: how mediation, accountability, and caretaking are being articulated in Flint, Michigan in the absence of a functioning welfare system; how the biomedical authority of coroners is deeply implicated in a lack of accountability for police violence; a comprehensive assessment of the environmental injustices of the US carceral system; and an inquiry of not only how to make prisons obsolete but how to memorialize decommissioned prisons as sites of violent heritage.

Participants:

Abolitionist Environmentalism? Querying the power of itemizing the environmental injustices of mass incarceration *Nicholas Shapiro, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)*

At the heart of North America's environmental and carceral injustices are significant accountability shortcomings. These problems converge not just in the hyper-policing of communities of color and the minimal policing and enforcement of the large scale endangerments of environmental pollution, but in the environmental toxicity of prisons themselves. This presentation details the first national study of the environmental violations of all of the almost seven thousand carceral facilities in the US. The findings indicate that the infrastructures charged by the American criminal justice system to be the infrastructures of accountability and repair suffer from massive environmental accountability problems. Our study indicates thousands of environmental violations of carceral facilities across the US, many of which were unknown to the US EPA. While advancing this new data, the presentation further details the potential shortcomings of this method. We will discuss the history of how conditions-focused lawsuits (including environmental conditions) that sought accountability and systems-change in court often enhanced the state's carceral capacities by leading to hiring more guards, increasing prisoner surveillance, and most importantly, building more prisons. In our practice we ask: what role if any does the leveraging of quantitative environmental health data have in curtailing the flow of people into prison or expanding avenues for early release?

Environmental Justice and the Relational Politics of Abolition *Elena Sobrino, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)*

The shrinking of the welfare state and the expansion of the carceral state in the United States has deepened racial inequalities and corroded capacities for creating and maintaining social infrastructures of support. Abolition seeks to relocate conflict mediation, accountability, and caretaking outside of carceral structures. To build "good relations" is thus a crucial step toward making the prison obsolete (Davis 2003). How are good relations

made in the context of chronic environmental harms and racialized austerity? Based on fieldwork in Flint, Michigan, a deindustrialized city surrounded by the Great Lakes, this paper examines how and why familial structures of care are on the frontlines of an ongoing toxic water crisis. Flint residents frequently frame their pursuits of remediation and justice in the context of familial commitments and roles, especially inter-generational responsibilities. At the same time, the pressures of organizing care work in the absence of a functioning welfare system generate complex contradictions and sentiments in response to the failure of the state to reliably provide clean water. This paper identifies abolitionist politics and potentials embedded in environmental struggles to redefine relations of solidarity and care away from neoliberal paradigms of community and settler norms of kinship.

The Freedom Mapping Institute: Community Mapping for Abolition across WA State *Carrie Freshour, University of Washington*

Where life is precious, life is precious. Ruth Wilson Gilmore's words, and all the relationships from which they grow, sit at the heart of the Freedom Mapping Institute. We aim to open up possibilities for radical care and interdependency built across people and places impacted by carceral geographies through community mapping for abolition. We connect the skills, knowledges, and experiences of human and physical geographers, abolitionists inside and outside Washington state prisons, and rural communities to better understand histories and ongoing struggles over the right to both the city and the countryside. This project takes place on the overlapping lands of S'Klallam and Coast Salish (Clallam Bay), Cayuse, Umatilla, and Walla Walla (Walla Walla), Coast Salish, Duwamish, Puyallup, Squamish, Tulalip, and Muckleshoot (Seattle) nations. Across the state, rural prisons are primary sites of state-sanctioned violence and premature death, intentionally locking up loved ones hours from home, bolstered through urban-rural socio-spatial divides worsened by COVID-19. Although this is what is, this is not what always was, nor what has to be. For example, the Olympic Peninsula once harbored radical Wobblies and EJ activists, yet today this generation of white working class elders have been pushed from timber industries to prison work at Clallam Bay Correctional Center. Can this radical history find light in the present? Why are Washington prisons located where they are, and how can we end them and build anew? Our aim in working together is to understand the interconnectedness of organized abandonment across disparate places while building for a world where life is precious.

Death within a White Settler Frame: On the Implausibility of Value Neutral Autopsy Science *Terence Keel, University of California Los Angeles (UCLA)*

Medical examiner/coroner offices across the nation are public-facing scientific institutions that attempt to be politically neutral and distinct from prosecutorial authority and law enforcement. Coroner reports and autopsies conducted after a death under police custody have authority at the nexus of public health, forensic science, and state law. This authority is especially salient for homicides not involving firearms as these cases present biomedical ambiguities that must be solved through empirical observation informed by the research, experience, and worldview of the medical examiner/coroner. This paper investigates the historical formation of this worldview and its larger epistemic environment as post-mortem medical examination reports rarely establish police culpability even when evidence indicates otherwise. In the paper I explain how the history of settler colonialism, white supremacy, and scientific racism have been central to the emergence and development of medical examiner/coroner science in the U.S. since the 18th century and continue to haunt the study of non-white death while under police custody. Informed by a collaborative data science project analyzing police death over the last 20 years I recount the

formation of medical examiner/coroner offices in Jamestown, Virginia, Los Angeles, California, and Wayne County (Detroit), Michigan, corresponding respectively to the periods of white settler colonialization, western expansion of American empire, and racial segregation. Considering this long view of history, I offer reflections on "the myth of the given" within science to argue against the use of value neutral forensic pathology and objective autopsy analysis as tools for abolishing law-enforcement related death.

Today's prisons as future heritage *Elizabeth Lara, Deakin University*

Correlations between disease, premature death, and incarceration have defined carceral regimes throughout history. Carceral heritage sites in California (e.g. Spanish Missions and a WW2 Japanese incarceration camp) offer precedents for understanding contemporary state prisons and envisioning their eventual closure. What happens when we think about today's prisons as future heritage? In 2020, California Governor Newsom announced plans to close two prisons by 2023, an unprecedented move in a state infamous for having perhaps the world's most expansive and densely populated prison system. Newsom and CDCR, the agency in charge of prison and parole operations, eventually announced that the first facility to close was chosen in part based on operation costs and "prioritization of public safety." Missing from CDCR's official news release was any explicit mention of the toxic, deadly conditions plaguing this and many other prison facilities across the state. As fiscal and policy advisors make the case for closing eight facilities, activists and advocates argue that these changes must come with reduced prison populations and budgets, investments in social services, and solutions for prison staff impacted by closures. In the struggle for abolition, it is not enough to close a prison. What are the relations and values we need to ensure when archiving these violent infrastructures?

Session Organizers:

Elena Sobrino, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)
Elizabeth Lara, Deakin University

Chair:

Nicholas Shapiro, University of California, Los Angeles (UCLA)

515. Wiring digital justice: Embedding rights in Internet governance "by infrastructure" - II

11:30 to 1:00 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Session subtitle: "Digital Infrastructures: Institutions, Capitalism and Corporations" This session seeks to explore how the language of civil rights and freedoms can be translated in the language and materiality of infrastructures and what the complexities are that arise from this process. As Keller Easterling (2014) writes "changes to the globalizing world are being written, not in the language of law and diplomacy, but rather in the language of infrastructure". From Internet routing protocols to network architecture solutions, infrastructures "set the invisible rules that govern the spaces of our everyday lives" (Ibid). The second sub-session of our panel explores the role of different types of institutional configurations in which the 'embedding' of freedoms into infrastructure takes shape, from the arenas of more 'traditional' Internet governance led by specialized institutions and often promoted through international technical standards to large international corporations that play an undeniable role in shaping governance practices by infrastructure.

Participants:

From Hammer to Infrastructure: Tracing "Breakdown" in Amazon's Vectors of Power *Ulysses Pascal, Department of Information Studies, UCLA*

In 1999, Amazon obtained a patent for the "one click" button. The same year, Susan Leigh Star published the foundational article "The Ethnography of Infrastructure." The essay extended

science and technology studies into the field of infrastructure studies around the notion that “The normally invisible quality of a working infrastructure becomes visible when it breaks.” Though Star did not intend to describe Amazon, the idea that infrastructure is invisible until it breaks is operationalized in Amazon’s obsession with seamless user experience design. What hides behind the modern aphorism that infrastructure is invisible until it breaks, is that Amazon’s infrastructure is broken, even when it works. When we fixate on the invisibility of infrastructure, we forget that brokenness is unevenly experienced. Differences in place, identity, occupation, and class engender different relations to infrastructure’s working. This presentation traces the invisibilized infrastructures that the one-click button obfuscates in order to better understand how Amazon’s platform profits from broken systems. Star’s study makes reference to Heidegger, calling infrastructure “ready-to-hand”—a turn of phrase coined by Heidegger in his philosophical study of hammers. I argue, under platform capitalism, a hammer must conform to the requirements of global logistics chains and the algorithmic rules defined by the platform itself. Before a hammer can be useful, it must be brandable, sampleable, reproducible, shippable, trackable, storable, packageable, reviewable, itemizable etc. A hammer can become a salient symbol the sited conduits, paths and linkages that comprise Amazon’s vectors power.

Good Enough: the culture of corporate software production
Paula Bialski, University of St. Gallen

Some practitioners have suggested that perfect software for a complex system cannot be guaranteed in practice (Collins et al., 1994); thus, releasing software to the public will always be done under a “good enough” principle, where every piece of new software can be assumed to contain errors, even after thousands or millions of executions. Based on six months of situated fieldwork at a Berlin-based tech company, this paper peers into the world of the often-overlooked corporate software workers. It sheds a light on an older, aging software development company to uncover how the notion of “good enough” becomes embedded in the software developer’s approach to their software and their work. Developers often spend weeks and months trying to deal with older legacy code and to figure out solutions to complex problems in large, complex teams, and resort to pushing out a software product that’s not perfect but merely “good enough” for their users—meaning “good enough” not to break down. Software developers often lose track of their data, get confused, get into conflicts, and ship software that is full of bugs, that they don’t fully understand, or that isn’t exactly to their liking. Such a focus provides a different lens on today’s software industry and gives us a unique critical understanding of the way our data is handled, and our software is built, highlighting that corporate software will always be just mediocre, or “good enough.”

The Politics of Protection. DDoS Mitigation and the Care for Infrastructure
Theo Röhle, University of Gothenburg

This paper focuses on Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks that render online content inaccessible by flooding servers with illegitimate requests. There is an increasing number of reports of such attacks being aimed at NGOs and media organisations, a development that is accelerated by the proliferation of vulnerable Internet of Things devices that can be recruited into botnets. Many organisations therefore rely on sophisticated forms of protection, provided either by commercial providers such as Cloudflare, Akamai and Google or by NGO-affiliated providers such as Qurium and Deflect. Following calls for infrastructural perspectives on communication technology in media studies, governance studies and STS, I argue that DDoS mitigation represents a sociotechnical site where new kinds of dependencies between media organisations and IT security providers are being forged. Despite their increasing influence on the distribution of content, these sites have hitherto largely escaped scholarly scrutiny. Based on an interview study with IT

professionals involved in DDoS mitigation, the paper focuses on the respondents’ perceptions of their role and responsibilities when it comes to protecting content. As a first exploration into the motivations of experts involved in DDoS mitigation, the paper contributes to a better understanding of the normative positions that drive technology development in this field. Furthering this understanding is crucial at a moment when distribution involves an increasing number of intermediaries with powerful traffic management capabilities. It also raises the question what bearing established imaginaries and visions of society can and should have on the transport layers of distributional infrastructures.

Session Organizer:

Ksenia Ermoshina, CNRS

Chair:

Francesca Musiani, CNRS

Discussant:

Niels ten Oever, University of Amsterdam

516. Plenary - Unsettling Science II

1:20 to 2:50 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: Auditorium

Plenary - Unsettling Science II

Participants:

Crip Maintenance/Maintaining Crip *Kelly Fritsch, Carleton University*

How do crip maintenance/maintaining crip practices disrupt and unsettle colonial apparatuses of science and medicine particularly in relation to diffuse modalities such as the curative imaginary, administrative biopolitics of disability, infrastructural violence, and broken ecologies?

Unsettling the Genome Lab *Rick W. A. Smith, George Mason University*

If decolonization is the repatriation of Indigenous life and land, then what does decolonization mean for the science of genomics and the genome lab, which operate as technologies and apparatuses of settler colonialism? How does Indigenous STS subvert the durable conceit of ethnographic distance in science studies? How do we draw near in genomics? How do we move from describing the conditions of genomic knowledge production to taking on the genome lab as a site of critical reinvention for the repatriation of Indigenous life and land?

Suspicion’s Unsettling *Nicole Charles, University of Toronto*

What is the relationship between suspicion or hesitancy toward medical and scientific technologies, and abolition? How might both praxes push us away from colonial curative logics and toward life-affirming institutions of care?

Session Organizer:

Kim Tallbear, University of Alberta

Discussants:

Marisa Elena Duarte, Arizona State University

Jessica Kolopenuk, University of Alberta, RELAB

Kelly Fritsch, Carleton University

Rick W. A. Smith, George Mason University

Nicole Charles, University of Toronto

517. Creative relations

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

This panel of four papers (with discussant) interrogates how “good relations” form, persist, and potentially transform disciplinary boundaries and practices between designers and STS-oriented social scientists. We explore the institutional supports, research designs, and intellectual dispositions that are best suited to cultivate “good relations” in STS studies of and for design, and also what new relations design practice might offer to STS (Murphy 2016). The panel considers a range of studies that are

driven by the rhythms, complexities, and stakes of designing and making buildings and objects in contexts of education and professional practice. Under consideration here are four papers – one from architect-educators and a second from social scientists – who worked together in designing, building, and reflecting upon a series of innovative grid-shell structures; another paper outlining a project that involves architects, computer scientists, and anthropologists working together to test the limits and possibilities of augmented reality in textile crafts; and, a fourth paper that proposes rethinking design education through the perspectives of STS. In reflecting on the empirical terms and conceptual challenges outlined in these presentations, designers and STS-oriented ethnographers point to difficulties and lacunae in the modes and temporalities of their research; in effect, “staying with the trouble” (Haraway 2016) to address how knowledge translations can generate productive and also challenging frictions across different domains of knowledge. The panel also gestures towards the future: how might such forms of collaboration and discipline-bending inform critical interventions in STS, architecture, design, and pedagogies; and, by extension, our shared near and built environments? Participants:

Designing/Learning with/beside: Technology/design studies
Ted Cavanagh, Dalhousie University; chris trumble, University of Arizona; Stephen Verderber, University of Toronto

This presentation examines the relationship between architectural research and Design/Build education. Currently, most education-based projects are modelled on practice. This brings in a set of implicit relationships to the sociotechnical. Architects practice a speeded-up ethnography: jumping scale, scaling up and down; modeling and positioning the project in the process of doing architecture (Norman 1999, Ventura and Bichard 2017, Yaneva 2008). Research parallels creation. The authors suggest a model of research ‘with/beside’ practice rather than research ‘for’ practice. The proposed research model is interdisciplinary and empirical, qualitative and quantitative. It produces both scholarship of design and construction, and design and construction as scholarship (Chi, 2001). The authors collaborated on a six-year series of interdisciplinary building projects involving the social sciences, humanities, architecture, and engineering, with all projects designed and built by students. The authors analyze a number of recorded examples of design / STS interactions that happened during the course of design and detail resolution. How does scale happen? How is the project positioned? How do different models co-exist? How do conventional occasions based on hypothetical, inconsequential studio models such as case studies, pin ups, desk crits, programming, and working with clients all take on new possibilities as time is ‘slowed-down’ or at least reallocated in a designerly way (Nicholas and Oak 2018, 2020). The presentation concludes by outlining the implications of considering Design/Build as a particular sub-field of the architectural discipline with its own scholarship, research, and possibilities for inter-university collaboration.

After practice: Messy relations in collaborative, cross-disciplinary research on/through design
Arlene Oak, University of Alberta; Claire Nicholas, University of Oklahoma

The Thinking While Doing (TWD) project was an ambitious “research-creation” grant that involved the planning and building of several structures by architecture students and professors. The grant also included two STS-oriented social scientists and two scholars from the humanities. Together the large group was engaged in intersecting and distinct modes of research, ranging from architecture practice to philosophical reflections. While there were intentions for the insights of the non-architects to extend and inform knowledge of practice, as the TWD structures developed, it became evident that undertaking diverse modes of research coincident with designing and building was more challenging than anticipated. This paper engages with the

experiences of the social scientists – an ethnographer and a social psychologist – who followed the design-build projects as they were occurring. By outlining how issues of temporality, translation, and coordination emerged within and across disciplines (architecture, architecture education, modes of social science) and their attendant logistics of practice, this paper delves into three challenges of cross-disciplinary collaborative work: temporal disjunctions between modes of knowledge production (e.g. design versus ethnography); possible mistranslations of relevance between the nature of potential insights across disciplinary contexts; and, the coordination of complexity across “real” architectural practice, STS-oriented data collection/analysis, and the constraints of academic institutions. By exploring TWD as a collaboration between disparate forms of research, each with its distinct rhythms, unpredictable engagements, and contexts of knowledge production, we consider how future configurations of “good relations” between STS and architectural researchers can be achieved.

Designing a research-creative collective: Auto-ethnography of architecture, computer science and textile design and making
Claire Nicholas, University of Oklahoma; James Forren, Dalhousie University; Derek Reilly, Dalhousie University

This paper introduces Gesture & Form, a multi-disciplinary research-creation project that blends design research and practice with an STS-informed anthropology of design. Gesture & Form examines the embodied nature of craft and design and seeks to model ethical pedagogies for teaching these skills with new technologies. The project explores these issues through development of an interactive system that uses augmented reality (AR) head-worn displays to document, encode, and later guide making at different structural scales: from beaded accessories to architectural components. The discussion begins with reflections from the core team – an architect, computer scientist, textile designer and STS-informed ethnographer – on their diverse disciplinary (and personal) conceptions of embodiment as an object of study and foundation for creative practice. We then turn to the ways points of disciplinary convergence and difference inform study design and methodology. The larger project distinguishes design research from design anthropology (or anthropology of the design process), however all team members are effectively participating in both dimensions of the project. To accomplish this, we are employing a methodology of collaborative auto-ethnography, where reflexivity and shared ownership are key. The latter part of our discussion dwells on the insights gained from engaging in this kind of project in relation to methods and research design. We touch on the logistics of developing human subjects research protocols, our strategy for sequencing the activities of design and research, the challenges of working across different technical skill sets and languages, and the blurring of participant-observer positionalities throughout the design and research process.

Collaborative epistemology: Building knowledge and good relations across social, material, temporal, and spatial communities
Steven A. Moore, Dr.

As a reflection of changing knowledge required in contemporary professional practice, and as a catalyst of such change, universities are experimenting with new curricula. This is particularly true in the design professions, including architecture. Becoming a recognized profession in the USA requires that practitioners demonstrate their mastery of new knowledge necessary to guard the health, safety and welfare of the citizenry. Some of this shifting terrain has been studied using STS methods, but the field is underdeveloped. In past decades design disciplines have experienced the development of at least six discourses that propose to add new or different epistemological content to design education, and/or to establish subdisciplines. These include design/build; educational design/build; experiential learning; service learning; sustainable design; and

Public Interest Design. What they all share is the experience of systemic stress related to expanded epistemological scope. If we think of the design disciplines as engaged in “composing” – buildings, landscapes, toaster-ovens – then we can conceptualize the educational stress being experienced in these new programs by recognizing that they require individual students to propose and control compositions with ever-increasing numbers of variables. Additional stress is added by the natural inclination of students to have interest in some variables, but not in others. The radical proposal made in this paper is to stop thinking about designers as gifted individuals and use STS methods to construct a curriculum based on the possibilities of collaborative epistemology envisioned in John Dewey’s *The School and Society* (1902).

Session Organizer:

Arlene Oak, University of Alberta

Discussant:

Keith Murphy, UC Irvine

518. Politics of data and quantification as modes of governing (Part 1)

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Techniques and technology have played a major role in the studies of governance ever since the pioneering works of Michel Foucault. Performativity of classification, quantification, and datafication is nowadays a central tenet of a number of fields. STS has showed how politics play out on the level of producing scientific knowledge, governmentality studies have studied the diverse locations of governing, and recent work in critical data studies, data activism, and data justice has shown the political and normative variability of data practices. In addition to this theoretical expansion, material proliferation of digital data forces more practitioners than ever to engage with the politics of data. They must negotiate the competing political pressures of participating in, shaping, and sometimes rejecting digital assemblages. Keeping good relations between citizens and data practitioners invites us to address the politics of data and its devices and techniques as a mode of governance. How do practitioners understand and navigate the political dilemmas of contemporary data practices? How do politics unfold, become visible, or remain invisible for practitioners? How are these dilemmas materialized in work, tools, and systems? How should we as researchers relate to such dilemmas? How does, if at all, recent attention to ethics and justice influence practitioner perceptions of data politics? The panel tries to expand STS discussion on data practices by inviting submissions that draw from sociology, political science, and media and communications. The panel welcomes especially empirical papers, but is also open to conceptual, theoretical, and philosophical papers that address data politics.

Participants:

Coordinating Data Collectives and Transnational Data

Worldmaking *Jonathan Gray*

How are public data initiatives implicated in different initiatives to account for and reshape the world, to make things global? This paper draws on research for my *Data Worlds* book (forthcoming, MIT Press) to examine the involvement of public data infrastructures in the transnational coordination of collective life. Drawing on social, political and cultural studies of globalisation, open and public data projects can be read in relation to research on different kinds of worlding and world-making projects – such as neoliberal marketisation (Davies, 2014; Roberts, 2009), platform capitalism (Srnicek, 2016), cosmopolitics (Stengers, 2010), the “Anthropocene” and “Capitolcene” (Davies, 2016; Moore, 2015), emerging “technogeographies” (Gabrys, 2016) and “planetary scale computation” (Bratton, 2016). Through the involvement of international organisations, multilaterals, development organisations, tech companies, startups, media organisations, NGOs and civic hacking networks, initiatives such as OpenStreetMap, OpenSpending, OpenCorporates, OpenOil, Open Contracting, OpenOwnership, Open Data Day and the

#opendata hashtag are giving rise to cross-border data communities and collectives for opening up official data, whether in the service of making money, transforming states, promoting democracy, gathering intelligence, investigating corporations, doing humanitarianism, building alliances, growing the commons or caring for the biosphere. The paper explores how different actors attempt to inscribe and align the socio-technical arrangements of public data projects with their diverse visions, values and practices in order to guide and provide the background for deliberation and action on the global stage.

Credit System with “Chinese characteristics”: Technological and Political Imaginaries of Credit in Post-socialist China
Yuchen Chen

This paper presents a historical account of how data-driven technology and social management met in post-socialist China. Specifically, I use the social credit history to illustrate three shifts from the 1990s to 2020. First, a shift of the social credit from a technology of market regulation to a technology of social regulation, which manifests itself in the shifts of the functionalities of the system. Second, a shift of the notion of “credit” embedded in transactional relations to social and networked relations. Third, a shift of the social credit from a modernization project that “learns from the West” to a credit system “with Chinese characteristics” (Lin, 2016). These shifts, I argue, converge and tell a story of the encounters and intertwinement between political legitimacy and technology in post-socialist China. Drawing from various sources including government documents, newspaper, industrial reports on credit-related topics within this period, I show how political and ideological orders across different phrases in post-socialist China spur adoptions of science and technologies in multiple ways and sites by different actors; and how technologies and data have been picked up as a fix and a tool in governance to justify and materialize political visions and subjugate individuals by redefining, datafying, and moralizing the notion of “credit.” This account attends to the materialities and narratives of the social credit in China across different phrases to complicate the understanding of not only the social credit system but also the algorithmic governance in China.

Reading between the numbers: Tracing the politics of data through the practice of data journalism
Srravya C, IIIT Bangalore; Bidisha Chaudhuri, International Institute of Information Technology Bangalore

Proliferation of digital data has led to datafication of knowledge across all domains of work. Journalism is one of the many fields to make way for the ‘new’ potential of data-driven knowledge via what is usually termed as data journalism. Instead of source-based news reporting, data journalists write data stories based on analysis of datasets, presented as colorful charts, maps, infographics and interactive visualizations. Data journalism combines statistical analysis, reporting and data visualization to find and tell news stories (Chris W. Anderson, 2017) and hence presents a new and emerging site for data politics. In this paper, we examine this politics of data through the practices of data journalism based on a 14-week long ethnographic immersion in the data journalism team of a leading national English newspaper in India as well as secondary research that draws on data stories, news articles and online commentary by data journalists and reporters. We highlight how access to data is controlled and negotiated through political actions, how data journalists leverage data for political action and accountability, and how consequently data and data journalists come under the ambit of political censorship. While critically analysing how data journalists, as practitioners, navigate the politics of access, participation, representation and interpretation of data, we foreground two important points about data politics: firstly, digital data as a socio-material artifact rearranges the narratives of power within and outside the newsroom; secondly, how the

larger social forces mold the narrative potential of data.

The limitations of data science in the non-profit sector – Why established political dynamics of non-profit data have lasting importance *Ville Aula, London School Of Economics & Political Science*

Although quantification has a long history in the non-profit and charity sector, the last decade witnessed new claims of Big Data and data science being a transformative force for the sector. This paper presents findings from an ethnographic and interview-based study of how UK domestic non-profit organisations use different quantitative and data-driven tools. Theoretically it draws from recent work on methods assemblages by John Law and Evelyn Ruppert. The paper argues that contrary to the public hype, the impact of new computational and computer science inspired practices has been minor. In contrast, more established ways of quantification, such as performance and impact measurement, survey research, and mainstream management techniques, still command a far more important role. The paper discusses how it is difficult for new computational practices to find their place because the established ways of quantification are not just isolated technical tools, but foundations that allow a range of diffuse actors to participate in governing the social life. Because quantification and governing are so closely connected, changes in the techniques are unlikely as long as the logics of valuating impact, measuring performance, enacting social phenomena, managing services, and attracting donors have such dominant roles in the field. The paper thus suggests that while it is evident that data science applications herald certain new dynamics in the politics of non-profit data, we should be cautious of reading too much to the technological changes and underestimating how the existing practices are intertwined with the political dynamics of the field.

Session Organizer:

Ville Aula, London School Of Economics & Political Science

519. Agrifood Futures in-the-Making: Part III

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

With a booming agritech sector, venture capitalists, philanthropists, scientists and engineers are playing an increasingly central role in shaping agrifood futures, both through the deployment of socio-technical imaginaries and the transformation of material realities. As a result, agrifood scholars are engaging with novel technologies including synthetic biology, tissue engineering, digitization, robotics, artificial intelligence and related fields. Scholarship at the intersection of STS and agrifood studies allows for critical examination of the tensions between agritech's aspirations to radically transform farming and food systems, and the profound ecological and social consequences these transformations might entail. Papers in these four panels offer critical insights into contested agrifood futures in-the-making. Panels I and II will explore what it means to engineer both the 'perfect farm' and the 'perfect food.' Panels III and IV will discuss contested ideologies and ontologies of food, agriculture and technology. These panels highlight the work of scholars affiliated with the STS Food & Agriculture Network (STSFAN), a small but growing intellectual community. We also invite anyone interested in our work to join our conference Meetup to learn more about the network.

Participants:

On Cow Farts and Climate Change: Social Media and the Environmental Impacts of Animal Food Production *Garrett M Broad, Fordham University*

There is widespread consensus that large-scale animal food production is implicated in a variety of environmental challenges, including climate change, biodiversity loss, water pollution, and natural resource depletion. There is widespread disagreement, however, about the best way to grapple with these problems. As with all topics in the digital age, debates over the best path forward are hardly confined to scientific journals, professional organizations, or public policy circles. Instead, social media

platforms like Twitter, Facebook, and Instagram have become key sites of discourse, as supporters of varied perspectives offer up a mix of scientific information, personal and professional testimony, and advocacy talking points to make their case. This paper draws from digital ethnographic methods and focus group interviews to explore this landscape. Building from the conference theme, it asks, what role does social media play in fostering or preventing "good relations" in the context of improving the environmental performance of animal food production? In organizing this inquiry, the work highlights prominent social media advocates across three broadly defined approaches to "greening" the enterprise: modernizing meat, restoring meat, and replacing meat (Katz-Rosene and Martin, 2020). Bridging STS scholarship across the domains of science communication, digital platform studies, and agrifood studies, the work examines the productive role that social media can play in educating and mobilizing networked counter-publics who are invested in environmental sustainability. At the same time, the research outlines how digital platform dynamics simultaneously promote misinformation, over-simplification, and outright vitriol that stands in the way of productive engagement.

Beneficial Biotechnology or Pandora's Box? Farmer's Perspectives on Gene Editing in Livestock Agriculture in Bavaria *Julia Feiler, Technical University Munich (TUM); Amy Louise Clare, MCTS, Technical University of Munich; Ruth Müller, MCTS TU München*

The emergence of CRISPR-Cas9 has recently rendered the large-scale genetic modification of livestock animals such as cows, pigs and chickens possible. Novel editing targets range from genes that curb disease vulnerabilities, increase muscle mass or convey hornlessness to the development of transgenic pigs for medical use. These new avenues for the genetic modification of livestock animals raises questions of how different publics, including farmers, will evaluate these new developments. In this paper, we draw on qualitative interviews with small- to medium-scale farmers in Bavaria in which we discussed the possible scenarios for using on CRISPR-Cas9 in livestock agriculture. We found that, beyond simply embracing or rejecting these possibilities, the farmers engaged in complex and situated evaluations of CRISPR-Cas9 that foregrounded the specific socio-economic conditions of contemporary small- and medium-scale agriculture in Bavaria as well as ongoing political negotiations about value attributed to farming, farmers and their products in society. The study points to the importance of exploring how distinct issue-publics evaluate the potential and pitfalls of CRISPR-Cas9 in the context of their specific lifeworld. It thereby emphasizes the need for future studies in multiple contexts and of diverse publics.

Caring for food is (not) caring for farming: negotiating urban gaze and (anti-)technology in regenerative agriculture in Germany *Mascha Gugganig, University of Ottawa*

In recent years in Germany, agriculture has grown into a fiercely debated issue among civic and environmental organizations, the media and policymakers, with various forms of expertise attesting how best to reform the agricultural system. While these debates often remain that—debates—Community-supported agriculture (CSA, or Solidarische Landwirtschaft, Solawi) initiatives often foster practical engagement among (often urban) non-agricultural actors and commodity crop farmers or gardeners. These exchanges offer a worthwhile perspective on agricultural reform, consumer-farmer relations, and the role of farming technology. Based on ethnographic fieldwork at a CSA in Southern Germany, this talk illustrates the confrontation of commonly expressed ideals and morals over 'proper' food production, and pragmatic day-to-day decision-making on agricultural practices, such as soil regeneration, in the field. While often like-minded in their approaches, health- and environmentally-conscious consumers, hobby gardeners,

ecovillage farmers, agricultural apprentices and students frequently find themselves having to align a care for saving food—often reflecting a romantic, anti-modernist/-technology ‘urban gaze’—with a care for a farming system—requiring a practice-based ‘slow gaze.’ These tensions further reveal that the choice of (not) using labour-replacing technologies and machinery, such as mechanical harvesters, may often directly relate to either fostering or precluding spaces for societal exchange on agriculture. Following the 4s conference’s theme of “Good Relations,” the talk concludes by discussing why fostering such experimental spaces of engagement are central for policymakers, farmers, consumer organizations, as well as researchers.

Farmers who tinker: Alternatives to incrementalism and the growth imperative *Matt Comi, University of Kansas*

While hop yards have historically been small-acreage operations with high levels of infrastructure, US hop growing has increasingly followed a neo-plantation model of high-acreage and high-automation farms. These large hop yards often have highly developed marketing and breeding components and these growers’ disruptive and innovative practices have reshaped the hop marketplace. Within this landscape are a scattered group of small-to-medium US farmers who also grow this labor-intensive, high-cost, high-infrastructure agriculture good. To maintain market viability and financial sustainability, these small-to-medium farmers improvise solutions, build their own infrastructure, gather and grow wild or novel hop varieties, and market their hops to an expanding network of local, national, and international beer makers. These farmers eschew many of the normative methods employed by large-scale hop growing, breeding, and marketing operations and instead tinker with inputs and infrastructure to improvise meaningful ways to maintain viability without growing larger. While many of these operations are medium sized growers, their ability to rethink the growth model of agriculture by engaging in immediate-term on-farm innovation and tinkering solutions illustrates how tinkering can operate as an alternative to incrementalism when considering stepwise solutions for improving financial and environmental sustainability in quality-goods and vegetable production.

Session Organizer:

Samara Brock, Yale University

Discussant:

Julie Guthman, University of California, Santa Cruz

520. Building a new heuristic: knowledge production processes in interaction III

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Participants:

Plan Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e innovación 2021-2030 (PNCTI) en Argentina: un análisis del ante-proyecto. *Judith Naidorf, CONICET-IICE-UBA; Mariangela Napoli, CONICET*

Esta ponencia propone analizar el documento preliminar del Plan de Ciencia y Tecnología 2030 elaborado por el Ministerio de Ciencia, Tecnología e Innovación productiva de Argentina. El mismo se define como un ejercicio colectivo de colaboración orientado a pensar en el nuevo Plan Nacional de Ciencia, Tecnología e innovación 2021-2030 (PNCTI) y está inscripto en el proyecto económico, social, productivo y ambiental definido en las políticas gubernamentales. Como novedad, el ante-proyecto plantea el alcance de un desarrollo científico-tecnológico orientado a reducir las principales asimetrías del país, generadas por problemas estructurales como la pobreza, la desigualdad social y la degradación ambiental, entre otros. En pos de traducir en políticas científicas concretas estos desafíos se procura la realización de interconexiones con el resto del sector público y otros actores de sectores estratégicos de la producción,

trabajo y desarrollo procedentes de ámbitos académicos y de la sociedad civil. El marco teórico que adoptaremos deriva del corpus teórico del campo CTS referido al problema del uso de conocimientos científicos y tecnológicos (Naidorf, 2014) así como las contribuciones respecto de la relación entre la política y la investigación científico-tecnológica para pensar la relación ciencia-tecnología-desarrollo en contextos periféricos y con economías en vías de desarrollo (Hurtado, 2017). La metodología se basa en un análisis descriptivo del documento preliminar. Consideramos que la conformación de un ante-proyecto orientado hacia las demandas estratégicas del Estado y al cambio estructural de la matriz productiva constituyen un desafío en materia de planificación de políticas científicas.

Scientists’ Interaction with Scientific Instruments and its Role in the Knowledge Production *Bahar Esen Özdemir*

Scientific instruments have long been a component that are studied concerning their various attributes in science and technology literature as they are critical not only in knowledge production but also being a center of attraction for interaction. In this paper, we investigate how the interaction of various lab members shaped around the scientific instruments. Our approach here is to take the laboratories located in Middle East Technical University’s Chemical Engineering Department as the study unit and follow the process of scientific work and interactions within and without the laboratory setting, aiding in the process of scientific work, in order to draw a picture of how these interactions shape the meanings of various instruments for different scientists. These observations show us that the scientific instruments do not draw their meaning merely from their implied connotation but rather from the interaction between the instrument and the scientists. These results provide us with a perspective on the factors that create that meaning and show us how the relations and the hierarchy that are arranged within a laboratory setting. Furthermore, an insight into how these social constructs within the laboratory affect the process of scientific work is observed.

Traversing Diverse Knowledge Settings: Constructing Professional Identities as Data Scientists in Nairobi *Ravtosh Bal, Independent Researcher; Matthew Harsh, California Polytechnic State University; Ann Kingiri, African Centre for Technology Studies*

Without degree programs in data science and the university curricula in computer science unable to keep pace with the rapid advancements in the field, university students and graduates in Nairobi are looking to settings outside the university to learn the skills to be a data scientist and address local needs. Digitalization and AI-based learning technologies with their potential for increased accessibility and individualized learning enable participation across these settings. We map the educational landscape of computer/data science in Nairobi and characterize multiple knowledge settings. These include traditional university learning, self-teaching via the internet (which uses algorithms/AI/machine learning), learning communities (which are peer-to-peer and mentorship based, but also draw on internet resources and traditional university learning), and communities of practice at workplaces. Actors traverse these diverse structures of learning gaining knowledge and expertise, teaching and mentoring, networking and collaborating, and forming a professional identity that is shaped by these knowledge settings with their distinct epistemic cultures. Following recent trends in STS that apply critical epistemic analysis to learning practices, we explore how people learn across these different knowledge settings in Nairobi and how professional identities are created from credentials, training, practices, and interaction.

“Wanted! Ottoman Strawberry”: Discursive Practices of Heirloom Seeds in Turkey *Maral Erol, Isik University; Müzeyyen Pandır, Isik University*

Heirloom seeds have been an oft-discussed subject in Turkey

recently, especially since the introduction of a law that forbid selling of non-certified seeds in 2006, and a new by-law that passed in 2018. As material-semiotic actors, heirloom seeds are cherished both by proponents of ecological diversity who are mostly considered on the left of the political spectrum, and by nationalists and purists who are opposed to importing hybrid seeds from Israeli companies for reasons of purity and national self-sufficiency. Both parties agree on their interest in non-GMO, organic agriculture practices, yet they have different motivations for desirability of the seeds themselves, and what they represent. As such, heirloom seeds stand in the discursive junction of nationalism, ecological diversity, sustainable agriculture, and food security. This research is an analysis of the discourses of the main actors involved in agricultural policies (e.g. Ministry of Agriculture, Chamber of Agricultural Engineers, Turkey Seed Growers Association, Farmers Union, and environmental organizations). These actors engage in different kinds of knowledge production about heirloom seeds through their discursive practices, affecting the growing, purchasing, and exchange of the seeds in question. With an aim to reveal the continuities and conflicts in the discourse on heirloom seeds, we argue that heirloom seed is a site for resistance for good relations between human and more-than-human worlds, even though there is a strong tendency to co-opt it for industrial agriculture controlled with certification and patents.

Session Organizer:

maria goñi, Universidad de la República (Uruguay)

521. Optical Media: The Impact of Visual Technologies - V

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Optical media, borrowed from Friedrich Kittler, is an expanded concept that connects photography, film and television with other techniques and technologies that mediate optics and vision (e.g. microscopes, telescopes, oscilloscopes, echocardiography, ad inf.). Normalized, expected and often desired, optical media shape how we perceive the reality that surrounds us, mediating our understanding and experience of our inter- and intra-relationships with ourselves, others, objects, and worlds. In so doing, they constitute power relationships that reify inequalities and uncertainties, the key themes of 4S 2021, rendering certain people, places, and things visible, invisible, or hypervisible. These issues have grown in importance in the wake of COVID-19 and social distancing, where optical media have become ubiquitous. This panel welcomes interdisciplinary research from STS and neighbouring fields that critically examine the role of these embedded and disruptive technologies in guiding our world views and relationships. By paying attention to the modes of seeing and looking that shape our perceptions, behaviours, and practices we can begin to better address their effects on other information systems including but not limited to the ones we work in, socialize in, and reside in. Questions we ask include how are modes of looking shaped by digital optical media? What potentials are there for visual manipulation, exploitation, or psychological vulnerabilities? What new possibilities for ways of thinking, interacting or organizing information do these technologies offer? Who and what is being rendered visible, invisible, or hypervisible and the power politics of optical media?

Participants:

Stitches About Our Lives In Times Of Pandemic: We Go Through The Textile To Take Care Of Ourselves, We Pull Out The Needle To Empower Ourselves *Carmen Gomez Vega, Bauhaus Universität Weimar*

Society is currently facing different challenges as a result of the sanitary emergency caused by COVID-19 in Colombia and the world. Women belong to one of the most affected groups by the pandemic and some of the most significant problems they confront are gender-based violence and the overload of care and household tasks. In this scenario, the importance of assuming equal responsibility and solidarity in the workload by men and women and the creation of spaces for networking to guarantee the well being of women become even more urgent. This work

discusses the textile practice and the digital appropriation as vehicles to reflect on everyday life during this emergency, as a form of (self) care and empowerment of women in the village of Dapa (Colombia) through an off/on-line workshop. Visual anthropology is used as the main methodological approach, in which art focuses on textile practice and ethnography on the senses. Research techniques include participation, focused group interviews and the (audio) visual. Its collaborative-participatory and de-colonial character implies that the instruments and the research process are put in the hands of the participants so that the construction of knowledge can be produced both by and for themselves and by the researcher. Despite all restrictions and regulations nowadays, this work is an invitation for an exchange among women, fostering ties of support and participation both in their families and in their community.

Visualization of Vector Space as Translational Relations-Making *Richard Groß, TU Dresden*

This paper examines the role of visualizations (cf. Burri/Dumit 2008) in scientific and artistic experimental practices as related to machine learning dealing with multi-dimensional digital data. Based on my own ethnographic research, I present two ongoing case studies, one of which is situated in an interdisciplinary laboratory of data scientists and biologists in Berlin, Germany, where research on the social structure of honeybee colonies is conducted. My second case study is concerned with the studio practice of a German media artist who uses generative adversarial networks (GANs) to produce visual materials for his video works. Both cases converge in that in each of them, practitioners seek to generate meaning by way of algorithmic operations in high-dimensional vector space (cf. Mackenzie 2017). In both cases, plots and other media of making visible or “revealing” (Coopmans 2014) the structure of data sets feature as optical media of translation. In this sense, I will argue based on my field observations, visualizations of vector space are a fundamental element of relations-making. The focus of my analysis is on the “data infrastructure” (Gray et al. 2016) of such translational relations-making. Drawing upon arguments from infrastructure studies, I look at how scientific and artistic knowledge, algorithmic architectures, division of labor, institutionalized expectations, and imaginaries play into the results of the practices discussed, and what is at stake in them.

Algorithmic Sea: Exploring the Critical Making and Seeing of Color *Gabriel Pereira, Aarhus University; Sarah Schorr, Aarhus University; Carlos Oliveira, Independent Creative Coder and Scholar*

How is the sociotechnical perception of color actualized through optical media? What do algorithms of computer vision tell us about seeing color? If, as described by Carolyn Kane (2014, p.211), color is not about vision, but about a “system of control used to manage and discipline perception and thus reality,” then how do computers see color? To explore this question, we combine artistic critical making methods and STS theories of algorithmic color, perception, and situatedness. Our installation “The Color of Water: Algorithmic Sea” (algorithmicsea.com) offers participants the interactive process of assembling a sea of colors. Participants are invited to submit images of water through an interface as they make selections of colors. These choices are shown alongside the colors picked by different AI algorithms, and are then added to a sea of pulsating colors. Inspired by the play of light on water, our algorithmic sea is composed of undulating hexagons, highlighting the flowing quality of color seeing (by humans and non-humans). Accepting and working from the opacity of machine learning algorithms, our paper contributes to contemporary STS calls that highlight the richness of partial accounts rather than catch-all calls for transparency, accountability, and explainability. Where Louise Amoore (2020) suggested “stay[ing] with the difficulty of intuiting what the model saw as a form of partial, situated, and locally specific account,” our work puts this into critical practice by representing

the color of water as something between differently situated accounts (i.e. those of different human and algorithmic perceptions).

Deepfakes and the Effortless Making of Fictional Worlds *Isaac Record, Lyman Briggs College, Michigan State University; Boaz Miller, Zefat Academic College*

Deepfakes, namely, algorithmically created realistic images and videos that make it appear as if people did something they didn't, undermine our fundamental epistemic standards and practices (Rini 2020). Yet the nature of the epistemic threat they pose remains elusive. After all, fictional or distorted representations of reality are as old as cinema. Existing accounts of technology as extending the senses (Humphreys 2004), mediating between subjects and the world (Verbeek 2011), or translating between actants (Latour 2005) cannot characterize this threat. Using the method of conceptual analysis, and employing the notions of artifact affordance and technological possibility (Record 2013; Davis 2020) we argue that the epistemic threat of deepfakes is that for the first time they afford ordinary computer users the practicable possibility to fairly cheaply and effortlessly make fictional worlds indistinguishable from the real world.

Normatively, a deepfake is epistemically malignant when (1) a reasonable person is misled to believe that the fictional world is the actual world; (2) she forms beliefs about the actual world about issues that are morally or epistemically important. For example, a satirical deepfake of Queen Elizabeth dancing to hip-hop song is benign because a reasonable person understands this is fiction. But a deepfake of a misogynic speech by Obama is malignant because it misleads a reasonable person about Obama's views of women. We illustrate how our analysis generalizes to other case studies, such as a Photoshop makeover, or a QAnon discussion group. Davis, Jenny L. 2020. How artifacts afford. MIT Press. Humphreys, Paul. 2004. Extending ourselves. OUP. Latour, Bruno. 2005. Reassembling the Social. OUP. Record, Isaac. 2013. Technology and epistemic possibility. *Journal for General Philosophy of Science* 44(2): 319-336. Rini, Regina. 2020. Deepfakes and the Epistemic Backstop. *Philosophers' Imprint* 20(24): 1-16. Verbeek, Peter-Paul. 2011. Moralizing technology. U Chicago Press.

Session Organizers:

Alexander Monea, George Mason University

Paula Sanchez Nunez de Villavicencio, University of Toronto

522. {From Industrial Health to Corporate Wellness: Histories of Body Measurement at Work

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

Contemporary interest in workplace wellness draws from a long history of efforts to maximize the productivity of the working person. The question of how the individual mental and physical health of a worker affects their output in the workplace has been an active topic of inquiry for academics and practitioners in industrial health, health and safety, organizational psychology throughout the history of modern capitalism (Murphy 2006). Insights from these inquiries form the basis for over a century of wellness interventions in the workplace ranging from motion optimization and menstrual tracking (Gregg 2018) to workplace wellness initiative collaborations with organized labor (Stapleford 2009). This panel will examine the development of institutionalized knowledge and expertise (Eyal 2019) in industrial workplace measurement in the fields of industrial and occupational psychology, organizational and management science, and industrial and labor relations. We will discuss how these academic and research projects are shaped by external workplace productivity demands under modern capitalism; how industrial health research shapes societal and medicalized understandings of labor power and what it means to be a productive worker (Lampland 2019); and the effect of physical and mental health initiatives in different workplaces over time, as well as their effects on worker surveillance and control (Murray 2007; Blayney 2017). We also ask who benefits from the commensuration and assessment of worker health and what alternative narratives have or could potentially emerge

around these measurements.

Participants:

Hormonal Advantage: Retracing Exploitative Histories of Workplace Menstrual Tracking *Sarah Fox, Carnegie Mellon University*

Tracking, Fox} Technologies and self-help protocols associated with menstrual tracking have gained popularity over the past decade, with wellness consultants such as Alisa Vitti at the helm. Through careful monitoring and lifestyle changes, such techniques promise to unleash an inherent hormonal advantage capable of curing discomfort associated with one's cycle and tapping an innate "feminine energy" to enhance work productivity. Though seemingly new, these approaches to menstrual monitoring have an historical lineage born of corporate management. In the 1920s, as a response to the introduction of white women into US office settings, company-sponsored studies of dysmenorrhea were used to justify paying lower wages. Other research sought to link absenteeism to workers' menstrual cycles and recover "time lost" represented by number of trips to the restroom and sick days. This paper examines how workplace monitoring techniques such as these from a century ago laid the groundwork for connected health- and fertility-tracking technologies marketed widely today. Now being sold as feminist, they draw on a belief in menstrual deficit, or an understanding of menstruation along productivist lines focused on curbing workplace absenteeism and enhancing personal optimization (Gregg 2018; Hoffmann 2020). In bringing together cases from over the last century, this paper seeks to establish a through line of economization and imagine instead how workplace tracking might be leveraged toward worker mobilization and bargaining for collective gains.

Digital Identity, Worker, Person: Assessing and Advertising the Self *Jina Hong, Informatics, UC Irvine; Margaret C Jack, Syracuse University School of Information Studies*

Workers in the US in 2021 are frequently asked to self-assess their value: proposing an hourly contracting wage, self-reflecting upon a performance review, or reporting productivity outputs. On a private level, assessing our value is important for our wellbeing, retaining and building on existing relationships, and ensuring personal growth milestones are met. Advertising our worth has become a critical skill in flexible work arrangements so common to the contemporary economic landscape. Digital tools have linked these processes to our online identities and Internet-based work. This theoretical paper therefore addresses the question: what strategies do American workers in 2021 take to assess their value and advertise their worth? To answer this question, we draw on Hochschild (2020) who suggests that self-assessment becomes a new dimension in the management of professional/private identity. We also build on Mauss's (1925) concept of reciprocity, we see how workers understand how what they have done for others is often the measure that they use to understand their worth. We also build on Henaff (2010) where production is defined by a productive culmination of labor that yields profit through a vigilant ritual sacrifice of one's own time, resources, and effort. In this paper we argue that workers' self-assessing and personal marketing behaviors are bifurcated between expression and management. With these behaviors increasingly mediated through technology, public identity becomes expanded into digital identity, and digital identity becomes the prevailing modality of assessment, which is edited to fit perceptions of professional normalcy and private expression.

Workplace Wellness Programs As Sites of Power, Expertise, and Discipline *Dorothy Rose Howard, UC San Diego Department of Communication & Design Lab*

Workplace wellness programs are employer-offered initiatives to appraise the health conditions, behaviors, and attitudes of workers, and to design and deploy programs for health

promotion, prevention, and risk reduction. They first emerged in the 1950s in the form of Employee Assistance Programs (EAPs), in which companies devoted resources to workers' addiction and mental health issues. Prevalent areas of inquiry today include: stress and coping, fitness, and nutrition. Reportedly, as of 2009, "58% of U.S. employers offered at least 1 wellness program" (Osilla et al. 2012). Worker health promotion services are factored into company valuations as a competitive advantage because they can lower costs in employee utilization of insurance, absenteeism, or workers' compensation. The results vary, but might result in the adjustment of human resources or workplace technologies. However, even while organizations may intend to improve workers' lives, these programs can be sites of the expansion of the control of work environments into daily life. On the other hand, unions have long demanded that workplaces take responsibility for the prevention of disease and injury among workers and in the process developed expertise (Levy 2006; Murphy 2006). At the same time, workers have drawn attention to how individual health behaviors and risks are not so simple, given the nature of pre-existing conditions and structural inequities. This presentation will focus on my recent research on forms of expertise that emerge from workplace wellness programs. To do this, I will reflect on workplace wellness programs as part of the history of industrialized labor and scientific management.

Measuring the Immeasurable: Fatigue Studies and Industrial Labor Advocacy *Vera D Khovanskaya, University of California at San Diego*

The question of what to do about worker fatigue has come to new relevance around discussions of "burnout" in the contemporary workplace (Han 2015). Work in STS and Medical Anthropology has long addressed the epistemological difficulties of translating illness categories related to emotional suffering, pain, and fatigue into measures and diagnostic tools (Scarry 1987; Bowker & Star 2000; Martin 2007). Efforts to account for worker fatigue in the industrial workplace trace back to the early 20th century (Gomberg 1948). The main outcome of early 20th century fatigue experiments was that they quickly revealed that measurements of industrial worker fatigue in terms of worker output were unreliable and highly artificial. These findings tamped ambitious efforts on behalf of academic institutions to commensurate fatigue. American labor unions struggled to make sense of these findings in terms of their advocacy strategy: on one hand, one could declare fatigue immeasurable, but then have it be folded into a general allowance for rest (which in turn did not account for fatigue, thereby erasing the effects of fatigue altogether); on the other hand, one could press forward with efforts to measure fatigue on a more physiological level, but this had the tendency to effect further levels of worker surveillance. Ultimately the unions wagered that in-depth measurements of worker fatigue at the brain level were infeasible in practice, and leveraged this immeasurability as a reason for unions to have a place at the table in collective bargaining over what Taylorists had believed could be measured objectively.

Error, Automation, and the Measure of the Human Operator after Three Mile Island, O'Neill *Christopher Allan O'Neill, Monash University*

The 1979 Three Mile Island Accident marked an inflection point in the regulation of automated work systems. Investigations into the nuclear meltdown emphasised the role of control room operator errors, interpreted by many as indicating a need "to eliminate human operators from such systems" (Strauch, 2018). It was in this context that Lisanne Bainbridge argued that such incidents actually reveal "the irony that the more advanced a control system is, so the more crucial is the contribution of the human operator" (1983). Bainbridge hence argued that more attention needed to be paid to designing work process and display systems with human capabilities in mind. Bainbridge and others contributed to a "Zeitgeist...in the 1980s... [favouring] a

deeper psychological understanding of the operators' cognitive processes" (Morary, 2004), encompassing the measurement of vigilance performance, cognitive load, and the influence of emotion on task processing. Véronique de Keyser (2001) argues however that this shift overemphasised human error as the key risk factor, such that broader systemic failures in automated systems have gone unchecked. De Keyser argues that the operator's "zone of autonomy" (2001) has been reduced, thus intensifying the irony that Bainbridge described. Contemporary 'decision science' serves to further entrench a model of the human operator as subject to the threat of psychological biases (see Kozyrkov, 2020). Worker monitoring and management based on cognitive models needs to be challenged in order to maintain scope for the creative intervention of human workers, which, I argue, is necessary for navigating the challenges posed by work automation.

Session Organizers:

Vera D Khovanskaya, University of California at San Diego
Dorothy Rose Howard, UC San Diego Department of Communication & Design Lab

Discussant:

Martha Lampland, Univ Of Ca-San Diego

523. Beyond Food: Perspectives on Practice and Relation in Agricultural Production I

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Social scientific scholarship on agriculture often focuses on food systems, but this panel addresses dimensions of agricultural production and practice beyond food itself. As pig bodies yield both pork and pharmaceutical materials, corn both animal feed and ethanol, and cannabis both medicine and building materials, how does the practice, governance, and commercialization of agriculture beyond food generate opportunities or challenges for emancipatory change and good relations? Well-studied food system concerns like soil and environmental degradation, violent labor practices, and the plantation logics of industrialism, might be augmented by studies that approach agriculture from non-food perspectives; submissions could address the complexities of agricultural production of medicines/pharmaceuticals, textiles, lumber, or other goods. How and in what ways do these forms of agricultural production generate specific relations with environments, social worlds, scales, industries, or practices of extraction? How can critical or ethnographic studies of agriculture shed light on linked or dependent industries such as pharma or construction? How is racial capitalism working in agriculture beyond and adjacent to food? What are the political potentials or projects surfacing in these forms of agricultural production (for example, climate and environmental justice), and with what stakes, tactics, demands, or effects?

Participants:

Agronomic drifts: the problem of nature for the alternative(s) agriculture(s) *Tomás Javier Carrozza, Universidad Nacional de Mar del Plata- Facultad de Ciencias Agrarias*

The global south is witnessing strong debates regarding the role of agriculture in development processes. In terms of critical research agendas at present, there are two main lines from the STS in this region: those who work on the role of productive alternatives, expressed mainly by agroecology as a productive system, but also as a system of values and beliefs. While on the other hand there are those who work on the problems derived from hegemonic agriculture and its consequences: extractivism, environmental degradation, among other issues. The STS have generated a wealth of research that led to an in-depth understanding of both agendas. However, the continuity of these readings and the repetitiveness of its premises and conclusions began to give rise (and resurface) to new perspectives, mainly from two movements: the understanding of the role of agronomy as a "scientific field" and the advance towards the epistemic-ontological dimension in the constitution of knowledge. Both issues have as a common denominator the tensions around the

problematization of the concept of nature for agriculture. In this sense, and based on a set of theoretical reflections and empirical approaches, the objective of this work is to reflect on the concept of nature in agricultural production and its role in extractive models and alternative agriculture. As a starting point, it is possible to affirm that the problem of nature for agriculture and agronomy is not only a research agenda to be developed, it is an eminently political problem and a central area of dispute in production models.

Exploring plant-human relations within produce supply chains at the Ontario Food Terminal *Sarah Elton, Ryerson University*

In the global and industrial food system, edible plants are commodity foodstuffs that travel along supply chains, from farm to fork. This paper draws on a one-year qualitative study of the impact of the pandemic on the produce supply chains that bring fruits and vegetables from farms locally and around the world to the Ontario Food Terminal in Toronto. Research consisted of key informant interviews and document analysis. In this paper, I problematize the commodity chain literature to question how this framework shapes an understanding of food and food systems. What are the social and political ramifications of thinking of food systems in a commodity chain lens? When considering climate change and the environmental destruction caused by the global, industrial food system, what possibilities are foreclosed by this supply-chain thinking? I argue that a multispecies and posthumanist perspective reconsiders these plant-human relations, offers a new paradigm for food systems and more sustainable possibilities, as well as good relations.

Nature, Technology And Society. The Narratives That Promote Agrarian Biotechnology In Argentina. *Sofia Curutchet, Universidad Torcuato Di Tella; Florencia Arancibia, CONICET-CENIT, UNSAM*

The adoption of agricultural biotechnology in Argentina in the mid-1990's, specifically the technological package composed of transgenic seeds and pesticides, has generated new and conflicting relationships between social actors, industries, and environments. The aim of this presentation is to analyze the narratives developed by international organizations, the State, the academic community and the business chambers that promoted the adoption of this technology in the country. These narratives address dimensions of agricultural production and practices beyond food itself and rely on a specific notion of technology and nature. Despite the fact that the adoption of agrarian biotechnology in Argentina brought economic benefits only to a small sector and implied critical environmental and public health effects, the narratives that promoted it are based on a typical idea of the "linear model of development": that techno-scientific progress automatically generates progress for humanity. Our analysis is based on secondary and primary sources. The secondary sources are narratives analyzed by other authors and the primary sources are product of archival research conducted during 2020 in the journals "Ciencia Hoy" (an Argentine non-academic journal where scientists publish their political opinions about scientific development and technological innovation) and "Red de Innovadores" (a non-academic journal led by an Argentine association of rural producers, which reflect about agronomic industry practices), and in the Ministry of Science and Technology's public policy plans.

"The New/Next/Second Green Revolution": Agricultural Technologies, Sociotechnical Imaginaries, and Social Transformation *Wythe Marschall, Harvard University, Department of the History of Science*

The phrase "green revolution" appears frequently in the discourse of agricultural technology (ag tech), signifying a technical "disruption" to food production. In the future tense, such a transformation is typically called a "new," "next," or "second" (or third, or fourth) green revolution. The notion of a single

"first" green revolution that occurred in the mid-twentieth century, however, has been challenged by STS scholars, who have shown that "the" green revolution was multiple, is ongoing, often failed, and cannot be reduced to a transition of agricultural knowledge from the Global North to South, but consisted instead of the co-construction of this knowledge in sites such as Mexico's Yaqui Valley. This paper traces the development of calls for a new/next/second green revolution within the discourse of agricultural technology, comparing the paradoxical uses of such rhetoric across its subsectors. In some instances, a new/next/second green revolution is envisioned as an extension of the "first" green revolution. At other times, such a call portends a counterrevolution enabled by the adoption of information technologies, controlled environment agriculture, and/or agricultural biotechnologies. Finally, for skeptics of ag tech, any use of the term "green revolution" is flawed. Prominent regenerative farmer Chris Newman summarized his critique in its title: "No, We Don't Need Another Green Revolution." This paper analyzes pro- and anti-green revolution rhetorics in order to illuminate how different stakeholders make sense of the role of technology in agriculture, and the links between imagined changes in agricultural production and visions for more sustainable and just societies.

Assembling Glyphosate: Generic Markets, Overaccumulation And Uneven Chemical Geographies *Christian Berndt, University of Zurich*

Putting social studies of economization into dialogue with political economic research on commodity chains and uneven development, the paper takes pesticides center stage. Rather than mere production inputs, synthetic agrochemicals are complex commodities that emerge in spatially fragmented production networks, move through expansive distribution channels and are applied in almost every corner of our world. In so doing they are key drivers of the global food system, making us dependent on these chemical substances as never before. There is no better example for this than glyphosate and its eventful commodity life. Choosing Argentina as an empirical entry-point, I start with the emergence of glyphosate as "a once-in-a-century-herbicide" (Duke and Powles 2008) in heterogeneous socio-natural arrangements. These range from other chemical substances, such as formulation partners or rival herbicides, to agricultural production methods, advances in seed science, and agrochemical companies and their market strategies after glyphosate moved from patent-protected to generic status. In a second step, I turn to glyphosate's change of fortunes at the peak of its commercial success in the late 2000s. After it had become chemically ubiquitous, its carefully constructed identity as cost-saving, efficient and harmless to non-human nature fell apart. This materialized in overaccumulation (economically and physically) and sparked resistance by nature and social movements. This led to ongoing attempts to restabilize glyphosate as a commodity, key agents forging new sociotechnological arrangements characterized by new chemical relations and new uneven geographies as global pesticide production, distribution and use increasingly shift to the global south.

Productive Noncoherences: Relationalities of Livestock Management and AMR Control in West African Livestock Sectors *Andrea Butcher, University of Helsinki; Jose A. Cañada, University of Exeter; Salla Sariola, University of Helsinki*

Antimicrobial resistance (AMR) creates challenges for livestock breeders in low-resource settings, not least their stigmatisation as problem users of antimicrobial therapies. Global policy for managing AMR defines problematic antibiotic use (ABU) as a result of a knowledge deficit that can be remedied relatively simply by educating users to make better informed decisions (Tompson and Chandler 2021). This model assumes that users (in this case livestock breeders in low-resource settings) have

unrestricted agency in their social and material capacities to choose. Drawing upon AMR research in West Africa, we demonstrate how for breeders, decisions to use antibiotics manifest in an ecology of production landscapes that limit viable alternatives. These include livestock management policy that restricts access to training and veterinary support, or livelihood and food security imperatives that refuse the possibility to improve biosecurity or observe antibiotic withdrawal periods. By adopting an STS-inspired perspective of noncoherence (Law et al. 2013), we examine the heterogeneity of materials and instrumental logics at play in situated livestock management protocols and practices which can influence antibiotic decision-making. We take this further to consider noncoherences as possibilities for accepting heterogeneity in a programme for change, and making global policy for managing AMR in livestock sectors more responsive. Do alternative information routes, animal health management strategies, or biosecurities exist, and what kinds of experiments are required to make them viable? By approaching noncoherence as productive moments of encounter, we draw attention to context-specific alternatives for improving livestock management capacities and reducing antibiotic reliance in low-resource settings.

Session Organizer:

Gabrielle Robbins, MIT HASTS

Chair:

Alex Rewegan, MIT

524. Knowing Platforms - III

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Ontological Structure in Digital Music Platforms *Katherine O'Toole*, Northwestern University

A challenge for many digital platforms is helping users navigate the large amount of available data, requiring designers to consider the cultural and ontological norms that will structure how the user makes sense of the platform. In many music platforms, users can explore playlists created to fit different styles, aesthetics, and emotional states. This creates micro-structures that represent the assessment of music artifacts in terms of associations with certain concepts. Analyzing this at scale, we generate a 'conceptual map' that illustrates the key concepts used to navigate music in digital platforms. Using Spotify's API, we scraped publicly available playlists by category, returning 48 unique categories and 1447 unique playlists. From these we extracted title and description, which were cleaned and tokenized to give us a list of non-filler words associated with each playlist. We then created a network, with each unique word represented by a node, and edges and edge weights indicating the number of unique playlists they co-occurred for. We then used community detection to find key word groups, enabling us to identify prominent concepts being leveraged for categorization purposes in the playlists. In doing so, this paper provides an illustration of how technology can act as a medium for the process of collective sense-making. This approach contributes to STS by leveraging network science to identify ontological structures that emerge in digital platforms, and to examine the complex role technology plays in both reflecting and shaping our cultural norms.

Opening the black-box of platform and make it much more responsible *Yuhan Bao*, Tsinghua University; *Yang Fei*, Tsinghua University

Nowadays internet platform companies are becoming key subjects in social and economic life, and also becoming subjects with quasi-public power and management responsibility based on their advantages in technology and information. In practice, the algorithm of the platform has a dramatic impact on social life. The relationship between online life platforms and delivery

riders, drivers is becoming a key issue in China. Based on the Actor-Network Theory, this paper reveals the black box of an Internet platform company based on the interview and observation of the internal staff, delivery riders and other relevant subjects. This paper holds that the platform is not a homogeneous whole, but a form of organization composed of multiple subjects and also a system of technologies. By analyzing the several cases which raise debates about the care for the delivery riders, drivers. We find that the governance of platform is not a work only oriented to the platform whole and each actant holds commons but differentiated responsibility. The relevant actors could open the black box of platform may make it much more reflective and encourage it to realize responsible innovation by entrenching the linkage with the actants within it.

Platformization and cultural Participation: ambiguities and Contradictions between Commercial and Institutional Platforms *Marta Severo*, University Paris Nanterre; *Benjamin Barbier*, University Paris Nanterre

In the cultural context, the platform has emerged as the ideal device for creating collaborative or participatory dynamics. Cultural platforms are generally spaces that allow contributors, also called amateurs, to express themselves by posting or commenting on content. Fans of culture, music, art or cinema have invaded these devices with their creations and critiques regarding cultural objects to which they are intimately linked. This phenomenon has developed in two directions. On the one hand, commercial actors have offered platforms specifically aimed at amateurs by building business models around their passions (DeviantArt, Wattpad, etc.). On the other hand, institutions have provided citizen with platforms (notably crowdsourcing platforms for transcription and indexation) to involve them in the co-construction of official knowledge (Zooniverse, Annotate, etc.). We argue that this phenomenon should not be interpreted in a Manichean way by opposing the bad commercial platforms to the nice institutional platforms. We aim at exploring the cross-cutting issues that these platforms generate and the ambiguities of their functioning. By focusing on the dynamics of design and use and by exploring the underlying interactions between human and non-human actors, we will study the status and motivations of the users and the status of the produced knowledge in relation to the objectives of the platform. By considering the users as potential free-workers we aim to emphasize the dynamics of power that rule the platform/user relationship. The case of genealogy platforms will be used as our main field of analysis through interviews with designers and users.

Platforms & Academia: A state-of-the-arts *Mehdi Arfaoui*

For at least two decades, the cohabitation of academic activities with a set of digital platforms has generated additional workloads of which contours are difficult to grasp. The place taken by digital work in the daily lives of academics is becoming even more important as the academic job market becomes more austere and competitive. In the meantime, worldwide governments and public institutions have encouraged the adoption by academics of a range of digital tools and online practices to increase their value and visibility. ICT – first and foremost digital platforms – then appear as means offered to academics to respond to contemporary imperatives and uncertainty. This digital “side-work” (“travail à-côté” in the sense of Florence Weber (2009)), which is likely to take academics more and more time but also to transform the nature and product of their work, has, however, seldom been the subject of empirical investigation. After having presented this phenomenon as the collateral effect of two major trends – on the one hand, the neomanagerialization of academia, pushing academics to adopt self-entrepreneurial strategies, and, on the other hand, the penetration of digital tools in higher education and research both as a requirement and as a resource for their activities –, I expose a state-of-the-arts on what I call a

"platformization of academic work" and a typology of the forms of digital work by academics, as well as a cartography of associated platforms and their business models.

Session Organizer:

Moira Weigel, Northeastern University

525. Struggles for Power, Legitimacy, and Control between Disciplines within Interdisciplinary Research Organizations - I

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

As the scientific endeavour is increasingly oriented towards addressing 'global challenges', interdisciplinary research organisations are becoming ever more important. Within such organisations different disciplinary groups collaborate while at the same time vying for power, legitimacy, and control. Our panel examines how these dynamics affect the work within interdisciplinary research organisations. Unevenly distributed power among participating disciplines and, related to that, divergent disciplinary (epistemic) statuses can for instance be a risk for successful interdisciplinary collaboration (Reich & Reich, 2006). Organization members might for example experience hindering feelings of subordination, or of superiority. And if an organization is part of a wider interdisciplinary field, 'disciplinary inequalities' within this field — such as unequal funding, publishing or job opportunities for members of different disciplines — could be perpetuated or have an impact on the social dynamics at the organizational level. Questions we seek to address during the panel are: What kind of challenges do disciplinary power struggles pose for the success of interdisciplinary research organizations? Might there be any epistemic effects? And how exactly do the dynamics between members of different disciplines at the scientific field level relate to those at the organizational level? Organizational structures are said to reflect the power relations among constituting groups (e.g. Collins, 1981), is this effect present in interdisciplinary research organizations? Even in cases where policy makers are in charge of determining the organizational set-up? How do, or might, research organizations mitigate — for social or epistemic reasons — tensions between participating disciplines? In which ways can STS insights, for instance about the hierarchical structure of scientific fields (Albert & Kleinman, 2011), epistemic cultures (Knorr-Cetina, 1999) or (other) laboratory studies observations on power struggles, inform strategies to deal with disciplinary power imbalances in interdisciplinary research organizations? References Albert, M., & Kleinman, D. L. (2011). Bringing Bourdieu to Science and Technology Studies. *Minerva*, 49(3), 263–273. Collins, R. (1981). On the Microfoundations of Macrosociology. *American Journal of Sociology*, 86(5), 984–1014. Knorr-Cetina, K. (1999). *Epistemic Cultures: How the Sciences Make Knowledge*. Cambridge: Harvard University Press. Reich, S. M., & Reich, J. A. (2006). Cultural competence in interdisciplinary collaborations: A method for respecting diversity in research partnerships. *American journal of community psychology*, 38(1–2), 51–62.

Participants:

Interdisciplinary Integration, Division of Labor, and Disciplinary Status *Evelyn Brister, Rochester Institute Of Technology; Marisa Rinkus, Michigan State University* Interdisciplinary research faces unique challenges when it addresses research problems that require integrating the social and natural sciences. Differences between sciences are not only in factual and conceptual knowledge, but also in methods, standards of evidence, causes, and values. These differences sometimes lead to misunderstandings within a research team that are more serious than simple miscommunication because there is no clear external standard to resolve them. But working through such epistemic differences can be essential to integrating scientific knowledge. We are motivated to investigate the connection between division of labor, integration, and disciplinary status because of the imperative to avoid integration failure: it is unfortunately common for social scientists to report that they were added to an interdisciplinary project too late to affect research design. The most common metric of interdisciplinary integration measures how widely and how far from its locus a corpus of articles cites literature across a

conceptual map of disciplines. It focuses on the content of research. However, such scores are unable to identify failures described by social scientists because they do not assess the quality of the process of collaboration. We propose that evaluations of knowledge integration for teams of different disciplinary status assess the quality of the collaborative process via the division of labor. We examine bibliometric data that distinguish between teams employing an even versus a parceled distribution of labor. We conclude that a more even distribution provides more opportunities to work through epistemic assumptions about methods, standards of evidence, causes, and values.

“A Culture Of Curious And Interdisciplinary Vagabonding”?

Challenges In Interdisciplinary Collaboration In Two Different Contexts *Melike Janssen, German Centre for Higher Education Research and Science Studies (DZHW)*

Scientific collaboration is considered vital to address complex challenges both in research itself and in wider society. However, collaborations are not only related to various advantages, e.g. synergies, pooling of resources, but also to tensions frequently revolving around trust, reciprocity, power struggles, or prerogative of interpretation, that hold the potential to create conflict. Likewise, collaborations oscillate between different poles, e.g. between inter-, trans- and monodisciplinarity, basic and applied research, or bottom-up and top-down research. In this study, we take this spectrum as a starting point to examine the determinants and effects of scientific collaboration in diverging contexts and embrace the explanatory role of varying, heterogeneous disciplinary cultures and constellations. Based on two comparative case studies in the fields of translational biomedical and interdisciplinary biodiversity research, we intend to elucidate three research questions: 1) What are the manifestations and sources of conflict in research collaborations? 2) What is the role of the disciplinary cultures and constellations in research collaborations when it comes to the emergence of conflict and to what extent do these overlap with other explanatory factors, e.g. gender? 3) How do organizations and individual researchers respond to conflict and by which means do they navigate and resolve conflict? To provide answers to these questions, we combine bibliometric data with qualitative in-depth analysis. This allows us to link changes in patterns of collaborative behaviour with the internal dynamics of collaboration that aren't identifiable from the published record, such as the reasons, practices and the policies enabling, pushing or impeding collaboration.

Professional Visions in “Team Science:” Practices of Translation in a Randomized Clinical Trial *Emily Claypool, University of Chicago*

The production of credible knowledge has been historically predicated upon the maintenance of trusting relationships between individual scientists (Shapin, 1994). However, with the growing specialization of scientific culture, contemporary large-scale social intervention research operates through widely distributed sites and less visible research practices, including a variety of differently—and sometimes incompatibly—situated forms of expertise. This presentation will describe efforts to collaborate and produce applied scientific knowledge across distinct scientific disciplines and professionals through the ethnographic study of a complex clinical trial to develop and test a social intervention to reduce opioid overdose for people released from the criminal-legal system. Extant ethnographic work on clinical trials has focused on the ethical implications of recruiting vulnerable populations for commercial gain (Sunder Rajan, 2007), and how western scientists attempt to smooth over these ethical tensions with the field sites they rely upon (Rayzberg, 2019; de Souza Leao, 2020). Less research has focused on the internal dynamics and division of labor within complex clinical trials and how distinct disciplines cooperate

across relational asymmetries and an absence of trust. This paper will discuss the ethical, epistemological and political tensions that arise between experimentalists and the burgeoning field of implementation science, which seeks to facilitate the circulation and adoption of interventions beyond the experimental apparatus of the clinical trial. I suggest that different disciplines and field professionals operate under distinct professional visions (Goodwin, 1994), with concomitant effects on visions of scalability, commodification and innovation, ultimately bringing into contention what constitutes the experiment itself.

Do Differences in Framing Affect Disciplinary Collaborations in Environmental Sciences? The Case of Forestry Research in India *Vanya Bisht, Arizona State University*

The Indian forestry debate has been stagnant in the last forty years. The fundamental issue in this debate is the directionality of power: whether the state government or community-based organizations make management decisions about the country's forest resources. The two opposing forest narratives represent two very different positionalities, with different histories, professions, sensibilities, and relationships with the forests. Assumptions about the perspectives and values held by each side often lead to polarization and further aggravation of the forestry debate. This paper examines the differences in epistemic framing about forest uses, inhabitants, and forest rights among scientific publications on the Indian Forest Rights Act (2006). This seeks to identify the systemic differences in power that different disciplines accord to different stakeholders in the forestry sector. Based on frame analysis of 120 papers, the results show that when there is a lack of understanding about who is saying what in the debate, and how the dominant narratives get noticed, while the narratives of the less powerful agents get pushed to the margins. Understanding the differences in how the forests and their stakeholders are seen by the different academic disciplines will be useful in fostering more meaningful interdisciplinary collaborations in environmental management, by accounting for differences in power not only in terms of disciplinary hierarchy but also in terms of how these disciplines approach the things that they study.

Session Organizer:

Richelle Boone, Leiden University

Chair:

Simcha Jong, Leiden University

526. Publishing Interdisciplinarity: Emergent Questions from a Collaborative Experiment

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

In 2020, the panelists began working on a cross-disciplinary special issue of a long-running and highly regarded journal in the biological sciences, *The American Naturalist*, titled "Nature, Data, and Power: How Hegemonies Shape Biological Knowledge." They imagined the issue would bring scholars from the natural sciences, humanities, and social sciences together to examine the role of white supremacy, misogyny, colonialism, cisheterosexism, and other relations of power in theories and practices of organismal biology. Assessing abstract proposals and reviewing submitted articles brought into stark focus the challenges of collaborating using what felt at times like incommensurate knowledge systems even when goals were closely aligned. The project became an STS laboratory of sorts, as epistemological problems the issue's editorial team had all read about became practical conundrums to work through. In this roundtable, the team will discuss how they navigated differences in evidentiary standards and what counts as a legitimate form of knowledge worth publishing, translated concepts and language across fields, and developed a journal issue that aimed to perform the sometimes contradictory expertise of multiple disciplines at the same time. They foresee this conversation contributing to recent scholarship on methods of mutual engagement, transgression and transdisciplinary knowledge production, and relation building (e.g., work by Angela Willey, Cyd

Cipolla et al eds, Cleo Woelfle-Erskine, and Max Liboiron). Panelists will also reflect on unsolved problems and ideas for continuing this relation-building work going forward, with an eye towards building a more just science that takes anti-racist, feminist, queer, and indigenous methods seriously.

Presenters:

Beans Velocci, University of Pennsylvania

Banu Subramaniam, University of Massachusetts Amherst

Ashton Wesner, Colby College

Ambika Kamath, University of Colorado Boulder

Vincent Formica, Swarthmore College

Nancy Chen, University of Rochester

Maria Rebolledo-Gomez, University of California, Irvine

Session Organizers:

Beans Velocci, University of Pennsylvania

Ashton Wesner, Colby College

527. Making Science in Public II

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

Participants:

Imagining and engaging zero emission citizens: the case of science communication in FME ZEN *Hanne Marit Henriksen, Institute for Interdisciplinary Studies of Culture, NTNU*

The research center on Zero Emission Neighborhoods in Smart Cities (FME ZEN) aims to enable the transition to a low carbon society by developing sustainable neighborhoods with zero greenhouse gas emissions. Through nine pilot projects, in both urban and rural areas of Norway, new solutions are being implemented and tested. To engage non-scientists is both a prerequisite and a goal in these pilots, but this has proven to be challenging. As the focus mainly has been put on how to create public engagement in practical terms, less effort has been made to understand what type of engagements FME ZEN's science communication can and should produce. In this study, I turn to the production of science communication in FME ZEN, investigating how employees' imaginations of the end users of zero emission built environments produce different representations. I ask: How do the imaginations of a public affect the narratives produced? This question is two-sided, considering both the production of representations and the type of engagement that they permit. The paper is based on in-depth interviews of both researchers and communication staff within FME ZEN. This material is complemented by a narrative analysis of both textual and graphical representations of zero emission built environments, produced by FME ZEN.

Programming engagement in European robot competitions: care, control, and the arts and crafts of embracing and bypassing engagement *Carlos Cuevas-Garcia, Technical University of Munich; Cian O'Donovan, University College London*

In the last two decades, robotics competitions have become one of the most iconic events of interaction between robots, students, specialists, lay audiences, and the physical environment. Robotics competitions aim to facilitate open innovation, to put the skills of the programmers and the reliability of robotic platforms to test, and to foster education, team development, and public engagement. However, competitions are not neutral events but are rather co-produced together with the values and visions, practices, assumptions, and interests of their organizers. In this paper, we examine a number of robot competitions supported by the European Commission that we attended during 2018 and 2019. Two of these competitions took place in the intimate settings of robotics laboratories in Bristol, UK, and Oldenburg, Germany. The third competition, by contrast, took place in a

shopping mall in Milton Keynes, UK, and hosted a larger and more diverse audience. We pay particular attention to the physical and semiotic infrastructures -- settings, devices, scenarios, narratives -- that gave shape to these competitions and analyze how these framed, enabled and restricted the ways in which robots interacted with their programmers and with diverse -- engaged and disengaged -- publics. We analyse our observations by drawing on the concepts of care and control, and develop the notions of "bypassing" and "embracing" engagement.

Science communication as a boundary space: an interactive installation about the social responsibility of science *Maja Horst, Technical University of Denmark - DTU*

Science communication has traditionally been seen as a means of crossing the boundary of science: moving scientific knowledge into the public. This paper presents an alternative understanding. Drawing upon a particular case of social science communication in the form of an interactive installation about the social responsibility of science, it develops the concept of boundary space where phenomena can simultaneously belong to science and non-science. In addition, the paper describes how the installation functions as a space for interaction between knowledge communication and knowledge production. The paper argues that we should understand science communication as a social practice, which allows scientists and non-scientists to cooperate in performing science as an important part of society. The aim is to add a new kind of analysis to traditional criticisms of deficit-thinking and popularization by asking what can we say more about science communication if we understand it as part of (rather than separated in time and space from) science as a social activity.

The Engagement Incubator: Embedding engagement within scientific research *Rhian Salmon, Victoria University of Wellington; Jo Bailey, Victoria University of Wellington; Maja Horst, Technical University of Denmark - DTU*

A substantial thread within STS and Public Engagement with Science (PES) theory argues for scientific researchers to think more reflexively about the political, institutional and social context of their research, power structures at play, and how these influence associated communication (eg, Salmon et al. 2017). This literature also voices frustration at an apparent lack of integration, acceptance and uptake of this scholarship within engagement practice. For example, Irwin (2008, 2014) asks, are we "moving forwards or in circles?" We propose that to move forwards, we need to move in circles, continually revisiting and re-engaging with colleagues who have been trained through scientific research and science communication cultures. In order to test our ideas, we designed and observed a 3-day residential 'Engagement Incubator' to workshop how PES and STS concepts could be activated and used by science researchers. The study involved nine research projects across a diversity of disciplines, researcher seniority, and project stage. We were also interested in exploring the role of materiality and design in bridging PES theory and practice, as well as the wider relationships between communication and culture in scientific organisations and their contexts. The concept was subsequently adapted and tested in a remote 'zine/zoom' process that was facilitated remotely. Participants reported an increased appreciation for, and insight into, PES theory, and its relevance to their work, as well as a greater clarity around their own project plan, purpose, and context. They also identified ways in which this process changed their engagement design and assumptions.

Translating engagement in the European Commission: citizen engagement and science communication at the EC's Joint Research Centre *Thomas Völker, Senter for Vitenskapsteori, University of Bergen; Ângela Guimarães Pereira, European Commission - Joint Research Centre*

Calls for more and better involvement of citizens in the policy-making processes of the European Commission (EC) are 'a la mode'. For the 2019-2024 legislature, president Ursula von der Leyen set as 6th political priority, a "new push for democracy". This renewed interest also manifests in an attempt to establishment of a Community of Practice (CoP) on citizen engagement at the Joint Research Centre (JRC), the so-called "science service" of the European Commission. The Engage CoP's objectives are to map, build capacity, innovate and implement citizen engagement and science communication at all stages of the EU policy cycle, from design through to implementation and evaluation. In this talk, we take this CoP and the process leading up to its creation as a case for exploring how different models of engagement are guiding the design and implementation of JRC engagement activities and how they themselves are translated in the process. Applying a co-productionist approach (Chilvers and Kearnes, 2015) we explore different engagement collectives and practices and ask how meanings of science communication and citizen engagement are enacted and translated (Soneryd and Amelung, 2016) in the JRC's initiative to establish this CoP. We are interested in the models of participation and democracy that become visible, the identities and subject positions that are constructed, and in the diverse relations that are enacted. We ask how these different models or imaginations are co-constitutive with particular orderings in this 'boundary institution' (Guimarães Pereira and Saltelli, 2017) at the interface between science, policy and public(s).

Session Organizer:

Sarah R Davies, University of Vienna

Chair:

Noriko Hara, Indiana University

528. The Imposter as Engine of Uncertainty - I

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Participants:

Anticipated Imposters: Cyber Security's adversarial sociality
Matt Spencer

Cyber security assurance is a group of practices that explicate technical normativities: the security of a device or service is revealed through tests and audits, witnessing and reckoning, a synthesis of evidence of good design, good implementation and good maintenance. There is a sociality to cyber security, however, that goes beyond the social practice of evaluation. Security is deeply relational: things are secure in relation to an anticipated and elusive figure, a figure who threatens to employ roving and inventive tactics to induce malfunctions and extract illicit (mal)functionality. Following a breach, this potential is retrospectively collapsed. But assurance is always prospective and anticipatory, responding ahead of time, accounting for an absent but potential "malicious actor" and their tactics of hiding, impersonating, spoofing and obfuscation. Recent years have seen significant attention has been paid to hackers and hacking culture (Kelty 2008, Coleman 2012) and to anticipation in general (Clarke 2016, Brown and Michael 2003). But the role of the anticipated imposter in the formulations of security is underexplored. Drawing on interviews with cyber security practitioners in the UK, I examine the question of "who technical systems are for" that underlies explications of what they should do. In addition to illuminating the nature of technical normativity, the anticipated imposter affords purchase on cyber security's awkward fixation on the security of technology: it is in relation to such figures that the technology seems to be the thing in need of being secured, at the expense of the securities of everyday life.

Buying Time: On the Temporal Organisation of Impostering
Ruzana Liburkina, Goethe University Frankfurt

Actors can only become recognisable as imposters if they have had time to convince others and gain their trust. Technologies and practices of detection seek to shorten this time span by uncovering fraud. This contribution advocates a study of their counterpart: technologies and tactics of buying time. Without them, it argues, there might be no such phenomenon as imposters in the first place, only blatant liars or criminals. In making this point, I draw on an example of successful long-term impostering: commercial banking of umbilical cord blood (UCB) for family use. Medical experts, public media, and STS scholars alike routinely point out that the firms opening “stem cell depots” for future parents make profits from promises that go beyond the evidence. Nevertheless, these companies keep attracting research funding and partners, investors, and clients. To explain this persistence, social scientists mainly focus on neoliberal subjectivities and their embrace of individualised responsibility for health issues. What is mostly overlooked, however, is the biobanks’ mastery of a technology of buying time par excellence: cryopreservation. Based on ethnographic fieldwork in and around UCB banks in Germany, I show how the capacity to create a temporal zone that evades the logics of immediate assessment paves the way for impostering to unfold as an admissible and generative practice. I use this indicative case to draw attention to various technologies and arrangements that order time in ways that allow and encourage actors in many domains of social life to engage in practices of impostering without being exposed.

Imposter as a matter of perspectives: insights from fieldwork on Refused Knowledge Communities (RKC)s online during the Covid outbreak in Italy *Barbara Morsello, Università degli Studi di Padova; Federico Neresini, University of Padova*

The pandemic of Sars-Cov2 has required considerable effort to cope with the scientific, social and political uncertainty that the virus has led globally. Moreover, also groups simplistically defined as 'anti-scientific' - antivaxxers, no 5G and conspiracy theorists - handle with uncertainty through different strategies. From an ethnography conducted in Italy, from January to June 2020, on the online communities that support the knowledge refused by official institutions, it was possible to observe the emergence of a multidimensional figure, who play a key role in the reconfiguration of the RKC:s the impostor. Assuming the perspective of the RKC:s we define impostor as who produce a contrary and not credible narrative of the pandemic to generate profit and damage the population. Hence, we focus on two relevant aspects: 1) the impostor emerges from specific socio-material conditions; 2) both human and non-human can assume the role of impostor. In the perspective of RKC:s, the objects, introduced by the pandemic into everyday life, are often seen as contradictory to what they are presented for: if the mask, for example, is presented as a device to protect from contagion, for RKC:s it represents, a symbol of domination and profit for pharmaceutical companies and a risk to health. Correspondingly, humans who support official narratives about pandemic are perceived by RKC:s as impostors. This introduces the last consideration: the label “impostor” needs a framing, which requires to go beyond the 'principle of symmetry', in order to understand the positioning strategies from the perspective of the communities studied.

On the so-called "fake students" in France. The imposture behind supposed imposters. *Franck Cochoy, Université Toulouse Jean-Jaurès - LISST-CERS; Ygal Fijalkow, Institut National Universitaire Champollion*

We examine the possible and controversial existence of “fake students” in French Universities, i.e. alleged fraudsters who would only participate in exams and provide “blank copies” to receive a scholarship and other benefits associated with student status. After presenting the phenomenon as it has been addressed in the media, political and academic spheres, we explain why the debate on this issue lacks reliable data, and we propose an

appropriate methodology to fill this gap. The survey focuses on the behavior of first-year sociology students at a major university. It replaces the practice of blank copies as part of the longer “career” of young people of often-disadvantaged backgrounds in the higher education system. It shows that their behavior is less the expression of an opportunistic strategy than the result of a lack of knowledge, a lack of social support, discouraging results and a medium-term process devoted to “finding one’s way” through the jungle of adult life. The authors wonder, eventually, whether the true imposture does not lie rather in the economic theories of moral hazard and principal-agent relationships, which lead to asymmetric and paranoid conceptions of society, where agents are always accused, without any consideration for how “principals” and related institutions can produce inherently reprehensible behavior.

Session Organizers:

Else Vogel, University of Amsterdam - AISSR

Steve Woolgar, Linköping University

Claes-Fredrik Helgesson, Centre for Integrated Research on Culture and Society (CIRCUS)

Chair:

David Moats, Linköping University, Tema-T (Tema Technology and Social Change)

529. Technologies of Policing; Policing as Technology – I

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Policing has always relied on technologies to assist in the spatial management and social control of populations. Recently, digital technologies have become increasingly central to police operations, which parallels a shift to more proactive forms of policing. Predictive policing, online surveillance, biometrics, facial recognition, machine learning, body cameras, gunshot detection, interoperable databases, and drones connect to existing police technologies as many departments attempt to shift to ‘intelligence-led’ or ‘data-driven’ approaches. With the current public crisis facing policing, there has been a growing questioning of the effects of technologies, computation, and data on practices of policing. How can STS approaches contribute to studying policing in its situated contexts, considering the uneven and often fraught implementation of technology? Given how little we know about what technologies of policing, or even policing as a technology itself can do, we invite perspectives and approaches that study the material impacts of policing. In this panel, we seek to include a diverse set of concerns and methods in order to reveal new depths and breadth to our understanding of how technologies of policing and policing as technology function and transform each other. These might include theoretical, methodological, or empirical contributions that, for example, historicize policing technologies (Jefferson, 2020); engage ethnographically with police officers, departments, or technology developers (Brayne, 2017); experiment with policing algorithms (Lum & Isaac, 2016); and more. Further, given the disproportionate use of violence against marginalized members of our communities, we encourage approaches that consider how to center resistive and abolitionist approaches in studying policing. Nick Lally (University of Kentucky) Xerxes Minocher (University of Wisconsin–Madison)

Participants:

“Barking up the Right Tree:” The Ethnomethods of Big Data Policing *Andre Buscariolli, UC-Santa Barbara*

The advent of big data has expanded police officers' capacity to identify reasonable causes for suspicion (Ferguson 2014). Instead of relying on situational factors, officers can now retrieve large amounts of information from law enforcement databases (e.g., criminal history, financial records, GPS locational data, etc.). However, reducing data into mathematical models erases the context in which it was generated, thus limiting its usefulness and applicability (boyd and Crawford 2012; Kitchin 2014). "Context – what was accomplished, by whom and where, how and why, all need to be recreated for 'the data to carry meaning'" (Bornakke & Due 2018:1). Then, how do law enforcement personnel recreate

context while using big data for investigation purposes? This presentation examines the video-recording of a CompStat meeting where officers provide a thorough explanation of how they used GPS locational data (obtained from a suspect's cellphone signal) to arrest and convict a prolific house burglar. Drawing from Ethnomethodology and STS, I analyze the practices by which officers make sense of big data, many of which mobilize ethnographically grounded police knowledge – i.e., "area knowledge" (Bittner 1970). In brief, what is known about and through big data is tied to contexts this technology is employed. In what concerns its use for policing purposes, findings suggest that big data evidence does not conclusively and objectively "prove" that the suspect was the perpetrator. There has to be interpretive work done to bring potentially equivocal pieces of big data evidence into line with other forms of evidence.

Screening Police Vision in Experimental Cinema: Ethnographic Visions on Patrol *Christina Ashurina Aushana, University of California, San Diego*

While scholarship on surveillance and policing in the past decade has taken policing's "new visibility" (Brucato 2015; Goldsmith 2010) to task through analyses of mobile camera technology (e.g., body-worn cameras) and their mediatized effects on both officers' and the public's perception of law enforcement, this paper approaches police vision through other histories, objects, and relations that pre-date the ubiquity of this mobile visibility: 1970s experimental cinema and its relationship to the police ride-along. By blending archival work in film that emerges from my experience performing ethnographic research with police officers in San Diego, California, this paper approaches the tacit conventions of police vision as a technology through the site of the citizen ride-along program and historicizes contemporary policing through mobile filming techniques in the 1970s. Here, I bring feminist STS theories of mobile visibility to bear upon Stan Brakhage's eyes (1971), an experimental film Brakhage shot from the backseat of a Pittsburgh police vehicle on active duty while on a citizen ride-along. I offer up eyes as precedent film work in the 1970s that coincided with developments in mobile filming techniques that would come to lay the foundation for the televisual production of the ride-along in syndicated television shows like Fox Television's Cops (1989-present) and its contemporary progeny Live PD (2016-present), and which also shaped everyday forms of racialized policing "on the ground" in sites like San Diego.

From Eyes on the Street to Phones in Pockets: Community Safety and Surveillance Through Live-streamed Video *Aparajita Bhandari*

This paper looks at the connection of live streaming and policing as a potential modern incarnation of Jane Jacobs' notion of "eyes on the street". Various angles and types of "policing" live streaming will be examined: live streaming as a surveillance tool of the carceral state, live streaming as a form of community policing, and live streaming as a tool to hold power accountable and "police the police". Drawing from scholarship across fields including STS, communication, sociology and urban studies I conduct qualitative content analysis on the recordings, examining both the video stream and the comments of live streams on three platforms: Facebook Live, Youtube Live and Instagram Live. In particular I draw upon the analytical frameworks of Foucault and Jane Jacobs to understand surveillance and policing through and on these livestreams. I argue that live streaming has become a fundamental feature of the built environment and infrastructure of cities, which must be incorporated into frameworks and analyses of urban safety. While I examine these streams as a potential instantiation of "eyes on the street" and countersurveillance I ultimately argue that both the ability to widely and instantly broadcast and the permanent nature of this content on the Internet have transformed live streaming to a form that transcends Foucaultian notions of surveillance and Jacob's

theories of urban safety.

Datafication of police work: unboxing the contested social practice of public surveillance *Vasilis Galis; Anda Adamson-Fiskovica, Baltic Studies Centre*

Digital and data analytics tools are increasingly being used in police work both for monitoring, preventing, investigating, and predicting violations of law, disorder, and insecurity. The development, regulation, and implementation of these tools bring along a plethora of matters of concern regarding their social, ethical, and legal implications. While primarily portrayed as a way to boost the efficiency of police work and to improve public safety, these tools may give ground to various types of social biases, undermine individual freedoms, and lead to excessive criminalisation of society. Using examples of digital and datafied law enforcement tools at different stages of implementation for use in police work in Denmark, Norway, Sweden, Latvia, Estonia, and the United Kingdom, spanning from migration to traffic control, and from facial recognition to automated data analytics, this paper aims to identify the cross-cutting issues highlighted by these cases by looking at public surveillance as a deeply sociotechnical practice. We approach this by critically exploring the following elements: inclusivity of agents and objects of surveillance; demarcation of spaces of surveillance; (co)production of knowledge; (re)definitions of public and private space; shifting human and non-human agency and patterns of authority; diversity of agentive experiences of, and responses to, surveillance.

Session Organizer:

Xerxes Minocher, University of Wisconsin-Madison

Chair:

Nick Lally, University of Kentucky

530. Dead-and-Dying Platforms: Technological Failure, Infrastructural Precarity, and the Limits of Archival Knowledge

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

This panel explores internet histories through the lens of "platform death" as a way of understanding how digital communities grapple with technological failure, infrastructural precarity, regulatory practices, power dynamics, and nostalgia. Collectively, the contributions address the cultural, geopolitical, economic, and socio-legal repercussions of what happens when various corners of the Internet fail, decline, or expire. We bring together five presentations that draw on different methods—including document analysis, semi-structured interviews, participant observation—to explore the frailty of platforms, their underlying infrastructures, and their trace data. Together, by examining the histories of the Blacksburg Electronic Village, Voat, Tightcircle, Nerve, PandaTV, and Couchsurfing, we consider and complicate how the concept of "platform death" can help reveal the Web's rhythmic temporality, digital media's constant reinvention of forms, and the collision of hegemonic and fragile infrastructures. We ask: What are the theoretical implications of rethinking platforms as killable, ephemeral, precarious, or transient technologies? What—and who—kills platforms, and in what ways can they have uncertain afterlives? What mourning practices follow the failure of a platform? What can conceptualizations of dead and dying technologies tell us about the Internet's growth and stagnation, its present and futures? What contested knowledge percolates when dead platforms are centered over live ones? What is (un)knowable about platforms that once were, and how can this knowledge inform our predictions of future technological failure? We aim to build community, collective imaginings, and future collaborations around a research agenda that centers mnemonic experimentation, research fragments, platform comparisons, and archival data.

Participants:

Abandoned Village or Proto Platform? The Story of the Blacksburg Electronic Village *Tamara Kneese, University of San Francisco*

Launched in 1993 in the college town of Blacksburg Virginia, the Blacksburg Electronic Village (BEV) was an experiment in community computing. Far from the cashflows and hype of Silicon Valley, the BEV is virtually absent from the history of virtual communities and the socio-technical shift to social media platforms. Through primary and secondary accounts of BEV affordances (Carroll & Rosson, 1996; Carroll et al., 2001; Wiencko, 1993) and the oral histories of key BEV participant observers, I argue that the BEV complicates divisions between electronic communities and social media platforms, showing how many of the problems associated with large-scale corporate platforms also existed in a small, rural, geographically-situated community network beloved by senior citizens, elementary school teachers, and college students. I show how commercial elements and platform attributes like data collection, commerce, and innovation were constitutive of the BEV from its inception. The Village Mall and applications like MOOSburg, a multi-user domain, wired the town. I also point to critical scholarship other early electronic communities (Dibbell, 1995; Nakamura, 1995; Nelson et al., 2001; Rankin 2018), as well as the limited critical literature on the BEV itself (Silver, 2000; 2003; 2005), showing show race, gender, and sexuality based exclusion and harassment were endemic to even the most wholesome seeming virtual communities. The lives and deaths of platforms should be understood within the context of local infrastructures, including regulatory practices and power dynamics. Such cultural norms and social hierarchies condition whether stories are told or ignored, or whether platforms persist or disappear.

Farewell to Voat: The Wayback Machine and the Semiotics of Platform Death *Julia DeCook, Loyola University Chicago*
On December 25, 2020, at 12 p.m. EST, the infamous “reddit alternative” voat.co shut down. In a post just a few days prior to the shuttering of its virtual doors, the co-founder said that he had run out of funds to maintain the website. Founded in 2014, the platform grew after reddit banned numerous communities in 2015, most famously r/FatPeopleHate. Although the platform itself never identified with a specific political group, it marketed itself as a haven from reddit, a true “free speech” platform. Due to this, it became the home of the subreddit r/PizzaGate, which would eventually spawn into the larger QAnon conspiracy theory, and effectively turned into a hub for the alt right. Voat now joins a long list of platforms that have met untimely - and in Voat’s case, celebrated - deaths. But the website is preserved on the Wayback Machine, albeit in pieces, where curious onlookers and former users are able to revisit the website, but in a scrapbook like capacity – unable to post or create, they are merely observers. In this presentation, I examine user responses to the announcement of Voat’s death, using methods aligned with patchwork ethnography and through the frameworks of collective memory and platform death while foregrounding the volatility of the alt-tech digital ecosystem. By doing so, I aim to contribute to a larger conversation about the sustainability of alternative online spaces, movement across digital space, and how the WayBack Machine and users engage in a nostalgia-laden semiotics of platform death.

Twentieth Century’s End: Associations and Experiments with Privacy *Bernadette Boscoe, Occidental College, Computer Science Department; Michael Scroggins, Department of Information Studies, UCLA*

Before the social media behemoths of the mid 2000s came to dominate the internet, a number of smaller social platforms flourished on the open internet of the 1990s. At this time, the internet was new for many, and so too was the notion of privacy in these new-found electronic spaces. These early social platforms serving as forays for participants to communicate online no longer exist, and their electronic traces are few. Through their failure, these so-called dead platforms can reveal digital remnants that were cast aside, to be discarded as newer social platforms rose to prominence. In this paper, we look at two

dead platforms through the lens of their respective founders’ privacy norms, baked into their nascent infrastructures. We examine Tightcircle and Nerve, each was a social space to communicate: Nerve was a New York-based salon website with articles about sex and love, chatrooms and personals. Tightcircles was a Hollywood-based group email system, creating intimate spaces for socialization. Drawing on de Tocqueville’s work on associations as the “mother science” on which the progress of democracy depends and using contextual integrity as a framework to reveal how privacy was prioritized, we find that the founders’ affordances in infrastructure for private spaces centered users’ protections above profit. Further, we argue that remembering dead platforms can help us imagine a future beyond the current era of platform capitalism.

The Function of a Failed Platform: PandaTV in Chinese Live-Streaming Ecosystem *Jiayi Hou, University of Tokyo*

The live streaming industry in China has not just contributed to the significant growth of social media entertainment (Cunningham et al., 2019), but is also deeply intertwined with various mainstream political agenda such as poverty reduction, rural revitalisation, and industrial modernisation (Hong, 2017). Rather than focusing on the dominant players of this emerging ecosystem (such as DouYu, Huya, Douyin or Taobao), this on-going study concentrates on PandaTV (2015-2019), an ephemeral streaming platform which was once widely anticipated to be the Chinese counterpart of Twitch but eventually shut down and entered bankruptcy. By using a combined method of document analysis, interview, and participant observation, this research attempts to unpack the particular factors and challenges that lead to the failure of PandaTV from three perspectives: (1) the material and organisational factors that structure the platform both as a technological artefact and as a business institution; (2) the cultural politics and precarity faced by the live-streamers’ community; (3) the political economic norms in contemporary China that constantly contextualise the development of digital platforms. Rather than using the simple failure/success binary opposition, the study explores the historiography of PandaTV as a platform in Chinese live streaming ecosystem (Helmond & Van der Vlist, 2019). In doing so, it first empirically examines whether and how PandaTV does not cohere with social norms at micro, meso, and macro levels. Second, it details the ways in which how a failed platform can serve as the other to demarcate itself from the successful ones (Gooday, 1998).

The Life and Deaths of Couchsurfing and the Changing Ecology of the Web *Attila Márton, Copenhagen Business School; Karolina Mikołajewska-Zajac, Kozminski University & The University of Queensland*

Both popular business literature on digital platforms’ ‘blitzscaling’ (Hoffman & Yeh, 2018) and social science scholarship on ‘platformization’ (Helmond, 2015; Nieborg & Helmond, 2019; van Dijck, 2020) or ‘surveillance capitalism’ (Zuboff, 2019) largely focus on ‘platform winners’ that manage to install themselves as obligatory passage points and, by and large, share the assumption that once dominant, the Facebooks and the Googles become too big to fail, too big to regulate, and too big to die. In contrast, we develop a framework for studying smaller – dead, dying, surviving, or marginalized – platforms, suggesting that they are uniquely equipped to shed light on the changing ecology of the Web. Inspired by Bateson’s (2000) ‘ecology of mind’, we pay attention to ecological connections and the ‘success’ of a platform as the ongoing ability to adapt to new contexts. Our case study is Couchsurfing (CS), a free hospitality exchange platform, launched in 2004. The research material encompasses a large collection of in-depth interviews with various stakeholders (founders, volunteers, employees, and participants), ethnographic observations and documents. CS’s turbulent history, punctuated by several near-deaths, opens a window into theorizing the broader changes the Web went through after the dot-com boom. We argue that

Couchsurfing's struggles to respond to drastic changes in its environment are indicative of the growing specialization of the Web with a single operating objective, which is to profit from user growth and traffic. The resulting loss of flexibility suggests a dire perspective for the Web's future potential to react to unforeseen changes.

Session Organizer:

Maira McCammon, Annenberg School for Communication, University of Pennsylvania

Chair:

Maira McCammon, Annenberg School for Communication, University of Pennsylvania

Discussant:

Maira McCammon, Annenberg School for Communication, University of Pennsylvania

531. The Biomedicalization of Social Medicine? - IV

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

Biomedicalization scholars have argued that studies of biomedicalization need to be situated in their geopolitical context and within that context's history of approaches to health and healing (Clarke et al 2010). Biomedicalization can be absent in some sites, or it can be contested by a diverse set of other approaches to healing (such as non-Western practices of medicine). Yet such contestations within the field of medicine itself have often been overlooked in the literature on biomedicalization. One such field is social medicine, a field concerned with the social determinants of health and the relations of medicine and social justice. In this panel, we trace the blurred and contested boundaries between social medicine and biomedicine. Some practices of social medicine have included at the same time social forms of care and biomedicalized approaches. Other social medicine practices have explicitly challenged biomedicalization processes. At different times and places, proponents of social medicine have argued that it has been too much biomedicine (at the expense of social, political and legal approaches), or that it has been too little of it (HIV treatment in low income countries, access to gender-affirming therapy). Sometimes, biomedicalization processes initially promoted by social medicine in the name of solidarity or health equity, have been transformed into more techno-science-dependent forms of practice, sometimes in stratified forms. In this open panel, we aim to explore diverse empirical examples of interdependencies, interconnectedness and contestations between biomedicine and social medicine in different historical and contemporary sites.

Participants:

Enacting the Polycystic Ovary Syndrome in Brazil: when biomedicalization meets social medicine *Lucas Riboli Besen, Universidade Federal do Rio Grande do Sul (UFRGS/Brasil)*

In the past decades, Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS) has been overdiagnosed in Brazil, leading to several questionable cases—at least when compared to the United States. For instance, in 2019, the Office of Research on Women's Health, which is part of the US National Institutes of Health (NIH), released an online booklet titled "Polycystic Ovary/Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS): Underrecognized, Underdiagnosed, and Understudied." According to it, at least 70% of American women with PCOS remain undiagnosed in primary care. However, such data does not appear to match the Brazilian reality, where PCOS seems to affect up to 9 in 10 women, according to local doctors. Considering these scenarios: how can patients be diagnosed at such alarming rates, in opposite directions? My research has pointed out that as the Brazilian health system is universal and free, doctors have been practicing social medicine through the biomedicalization of women's bodies. As its main symptoms are outside Brazilian beauty standards (body hair, overweight, acne), health professionals diagnose and treat PCOS as part of the affective economy produced by beauty. By prescribing the Pill based on its off-label effects, doctors enable women to use

biomedical treatments as acts of aesthetic citizenship, allowing them to have fairer chances in social-economical mobility. So, biomedicalization is linked to the universal healthcare access promulgated by the Brazilian Federal Constitution, centered on social medicine. Thus, PCOS becomes an equalizer of opportunities as it expands off-label uses of hormonal treatments.

The 'construction' of GE mosquitoes as the solution to mosquito-borne diseases: Ethico-political and epistemic issues *zahra meghani, University of Rhode Island*

This presentation will examine scientific papers by genetic engineers that 'construct' genetically engineered (GE) mosquitoes with gene drives (a form of synthetic biology) as the solution to the high incidence of mosquito-borne diseases in certain socio-economically marginalized regions of low-income countries. A defining characteristic of such papers is that they 'biologize' (or 'naturalize') the public health problem of vector-borne diseases. They do not appropriately acknowledge the structural, systemic factors that are partially responsible for the public health problems that disproportionately affect the poor. They also do not acknowledge that the vulnerability of persons to mosquito-borne diseases, their experience of illnesses, and their capacity to recover from them is not a purely biological matter. Scientific narratives that biologize the high incidence of mosquito-borne diseases in poorer communities in regions of the global South pose the disease vector or the pathogen as the logical point of intervention. They create the impression that the only (or most) effective way to reduce the prevalence of mosquito-borne diseases is to use patented high tech scientific-technological interventions that target the disease vectors or the pathogens. This presentation will analyze the epistemic and ethico-political significance of such synthetic biology construction projects in the pages of scientific journals. Specifically, it will discuss the tension between that approach to addressing mosquito-borne diseases and the World Health Organization's WASH initiative that recognizes the socio-economic determinants of vector-borne diseases.

Theorizing Trans-Intersex Nexus- The Biomedical Management of Trans and Intersex through the Brain *Thelma Wang*

There is now an abundance of neuroscientific research seeking to pin down the origins of gender identity of transgender people in the brain. The established premise is that transgender people have a brain structure more in line with the sex group that they identify as than the one that they are assigned in at birth. This research aims to critically interrogate the neuroscientific notion of "transgender as brain intersex" by situating the neuroscientific understanding of trans people within the genealogy of the medical management of transgender and intersex people, and examining how medical authority consolidates itself through the "trans-intersex nexus", a mechanism in which trans and intersex people are placed in a relationship of simultaneous separation and reinforcement under the control of medical knowledge and technologies. This research will speak to the ways that brain science, cultural assumptions of sex and gender, sexual politics come into the interactions with each other.

Session Organizer:

Anne Lie

Chair:

Michael N. Healey, Johns Hopkins University

Discussant:

Jennifer Fishman, Biomedical Ethics Unit, McGill University

532. 4S Business Meeting

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 25

The annual Business Meeting of the 4S Council.

Session Organizer:

Stephen Zehr, Univ. Southern Indiana

Chair:

Joan Fujimura, University Of Wisconsin-Madison

533. Total Institutions: Technosciences of Care and Control IV

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Erving Goffman (1961) called both prisons and psychiatric wards “total institutions,” gesturing to the intertwined nature of care, capture, and control in efforts to manage deviance of the soul, psyche, or self. This panel investigates institutions and techniques of mental health care in the Global North, South, and colonial contexts, grappling with the criminological, forensic, pastoral and penal impulses of the psy-disciplines. Building from the work of feminist science and technology studies, abolitionist scholarship (Wang 2018), studies of racial capitalism (Robinson 1983), and historical and sociological studies of psychiatry, social services, and the prison industrial complex (Roberts 2001, Metz 2010, Ryan Hatch 2019, Raz 2020, Smith 2020), panelists will explore the connective tissue between the prison and the asylum, probing the practices, histories, expertise and apparatuses within the mental health care professions and other social services (from psychiatry, psychology, psychotherapy, and beyond) that knit together the carceral with the biomedical.

Participants:

Screening Mother, Coding Baby: Videography & the Pre-History of Emotion Recognition in the Clinic *Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley*

For over a century, the tradition of psychologists and pediatricians performing infant observation has generated norms for diagnosis and screening of a variety of maternal and infant pathologies, along with corollary advice for parents on how to raise emotionally healthy babies. This art of “baby watching” changed radically with the advent of videotaping. Starting in the 1970s, this new medium and new evidential regime greatly enhanced the data-gathering capabilities of clinical psychologists’ clinics without removing bias. The detail-oriented practice of coding the faces and behaviors of videotaped mothers and children did more than just render so-called invisible disabilities visible: new diagnostic categories and their criteria were developed out of this closer, pausable, and reviewable form of looking. Videography in the clinic allowed for the eventual coding and typing and pathologizing of “bad” mothers and “good” mothers, “sick” mothers and “well” mothers, “secure” infants and “anxious” infants (as in the studies of Ainsworth & Bell, Bebe, and Tronick). “Screening Mother, Coding Baby” offers a pre-history of facial recognition, data coding, and diagnostic algorithms in the relationship between mother and child. I argue that the new diagnostic categories and screening capabilities resulting from clinical videography work in two ways. At their best, they still preserve definitional problems and offer diagnostic criteria so that caregivers can receive help—either for themselves or their babies. At their worst, they create the ideal image—literally—of mothering or infant states as well as stigmatized distances from that ideal. While beneficial for screening large numbers of mothers for, as just one example, postpartum depression, this way of looking at and recording mothers also creates an atmosphere of surveillance—mothers, once under care, are also at risk for social and state intervention, and unevenly so across intersectional lines. Even after the actual video equipment is put away, a visual comparative framework instructs that a good mother looks like x, not y. The sample populations of these videos are narrow: nearly always white, middle or upper class, neurotypical (a “normal” mother). As this surveillance paradigm has given way to the training of algorithms on mass facial recognition datasets, neuroimaging, and other high-tech solutions to the problem of screening mothers and their children, these formalized diagnostic criteria, and their pathological norming, have extended their reach, becoming a dragnet that further encodes racial and classed biases elaborated nearly fifty years ago.

Stressed and Suspect: The Criminological Creep of Psychiatric Voice Biometrics *Beth Semel, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)*

From start-ups to academic research laboratories, growing numbers of psychiatric and engineering professionals approach speech as an untapped source of data about mental illness. Citing clinical wisdom on the audible dimensions of symptom manifestation, they aim to apply computational techniques to identify supposedly objective, biological indicators of psychopathology in the materiality of the voice. In turn, they underline the humanitarian potential of speech-monitoring technologies like the Amazon Echo, framing their ability to expand the reach of careful, clinical vigilance as key to democratizing healthcare access. I upend the “feel-good grammar” (Benjamin 2019, 9) that structures these accounts by analyzing a contested antecedent of psychiatric voice biometrics: the Psychological Stress Evaluator (PSE). A briefcase-sized device developed by the U.S. military to interrogate war prisoners in the 1960s, the PSE was subsequently sold to police precincts, storeowners, clinical institutions, and private investigators as a wireless alternative to the polygraph that could detect deception without a speaker knowing and regardless of the language spoken. Drawing from archival research on public debates and activist campaigns against the PSE, I show how it was used to naturalize distressed responses to state surveillance and violence as suspicious, watch-worthy deviance, bolstering scientific racist and eugenicist theories of inborn criminality. I argue that the benevolent sheen of contemporary voice analysis technologies obscures the technoscientific and political-economic causeways between the colonial, carceral, and psychiatric that they benefit from and slide across. I conclude by attuning to possibilities for jamming and re-routing the signals of these auditory surveillance networks.

Visualizing Corporate Ecologies in the Carceral State *Anthony Ryan Hatch, Wesleyan University*

By providing food and pharmaceutical commodities to imprisoned people, the carceral state attempts to meet its constitutional obligations to provide for basic human sustenance, but it cannot do this in a weak business environment. This project aims to visualize the private corporations that do business in the carceral state, and through that visualization I draw attention to the design features of carcerality, open possibilities for anti-capitalist and abolitionist responses to mass captivity. The prison is a specialized operating environment that is designed, in part, to facilitate the flow of commodities through the foods and pharmaceuticals through imprisoned people, a movement of biotechnologies that creates patterned effects on bodies and larger ecologies. Foods and pharmaceuticals reconfigure the body-minds of imprisoned people as they are forced to live in corporate ecologies as consumers within carceral space. Moreover, the circulation of industrialized quantities of food and pharmaceuticals through prisons (and all the processes of production, transportation, processing, distribution, and waste that circulation entails) creates ecological and metabolic externalities that contribute to human suffering, systematic environmental degradation, and climate change. I analyze how prisons private structures of commodity provision within carceral institutions are linked the raw needs for human and planetary survival.

Compulsory Nutritionism Across “Curative” and Punitive Terrains: On Nutritional Psychiatry, Nutritional Punishment, and Biomedicine *Maggie Mang*

This paper begins with two seemingly unrelated phenomena. First, the rise of nutritional psychiatry, as explored by Felice Jacka, to describe the nascent linkages between nutrition and mental health treatment. Second, an attention towards food politics and nutrition science as it functions within prison food regimes as technologies of control, reflecting Anthony Hatch’s

work on “nutritional punishment.” In this paper, I argue that food and nutrition is an everyday, political practice that coheres and is cohered by totalizing institutions and is a richly generative point of analysis that interrogates linkages between carcerality and institutionalization (Ben-Mosche); punishment and care; and the various ways at which deviance, difference, and (un)wellness are managed biomedically. Rather than focusing on nutrition science itself, in this paper I follow logics of nutritionism (Scrinis) as they have historically and contemporaneously functioned across “curative” and punitive terrains. I argue that the discourses of nutritional psychiatry lend themselves toward racialized compulsory wellness, eliding alternative models of mental (un)wellness that do not solely focus on the biological management of “disease,” as found within Mad, crip, and queer of color critique. Furthermore, nutritionism has a longstanding history within institutions (schools, prisons, hospitals) as a focal point for the enactment of biopolitical control. That prison food, and their patchworked regulation, does not fall under a coherent jurisdiction like the Food and Drug Administration is indicative of its use as punishment. Borrowing from STS, critical disability, and critical carceral studies, I ask the question, what are the carceral dimensions of compulsory nutritionism? Works Cited: Ben-Moshe, Liat. *Decarcerating disability: Deinstitutionalization and prison abolition*. U of Minnesota Press, 2020. Jacka, Felice N. "Nutritional psychiatry: where to next?." *EBioMedicine* 17 (2017): 24-29. Hatch, Anthony Ryan. "3) Billions Served: Prison Food Regimes, Nutritional Punishment, and Gastronomical Resistance" In *Captivating Technology*, pp. 67-84. Duke University Press, 2019. Scrinis, Gyorgy. *Nutritionism: The science and politics of dietary advice*. Columbia University Press, 2013.

Session Organizer:

Beth Semel, Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT)

Chair:

Hannah Zeavin, UC Berkeley

534. Do We Expect Scientists to Care?

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

This panel explores what we expect of scientists when we talk about care, particularly in the context of practical applications of STS such as training, education, or interdisciplinary research. Much has been written of late about care as a way of figuring responsible relationships and practices in science. Care is proposed as an organising device which, in acknowledging the interdependence of humans and nonhumans and the diversity of their needs, can promote attention to those needs and the development of more compassionate and nurturing worlds. This notion of care is inspiring, but what do we actually expect of scientists when we ask that they care? In this panel, we aim to explore encounters between scientific and STS communities where our expectations that scientists care are made explicit. These encounters consist of interdisciplinary research, science education, ethical controversies, crisis research and other avenues where we foreground our expectations that scientists care. The aim is to try to bring our expectations into focus, helping us to better engage with scientists and to work alongside them to develop more caring worlds.

Participants:

Future Scientists Are Usually not Expected to Care, But They Do
Audrey Groleau, Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières;
Gabriel Lecompte, Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières;
Jolyane Dampousse, Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières
 Scientists are usually not trained to care about others or to take care of others. In the Canadian province of Québec, this issue has been addressed during consultations regarding the new CEGEP (grades 12 and 13) natural science program, a few years ago. University professors in health-related fields wanted CEGEP science students to be trained in counselling, to be prepared to care and take care. Even if science university professors did not think this kind of preparation was irrelevant, they did not

consider it necessary, as this training is usually not part of university science programs. In the fall of 2020, we conducted a study on future scientists’ views of the management of the Covid-19 pandemic. Twelve university students enrolled in a science program took part in an individual semi-structured interview that lasted between 19 and 52 minutes. We noticed that the idea of taking care of different groups of social actors occupied an important part of the students’ speech. They explicitly spoke about this idea while describing interactions between social groups, but also while explaining the roles they assigned to members of those groups. Moreover, in their personal and professional lives, they often assigned to themselves the role of taking care of their loved ones, clients or patients. During our communication, we will present the results of the research related to the idea of care. We will also discuss the implications of this research on the training of scientists.

Collaborating with Plants: Plant Cognition Research and its Critics
Delia Gavrus, University of Winnipeg; Vivien Hamilton, Harvey Mudd College

Recently, some biologists have begun to argue that plants can communicate, remember, and make decisions. These claims have been met with fierce criticism from other scientists who argue that attributing cognition to plants is inappropriate. Without the complex brain structures of animals, it is impossible for plants to be conscious (Taiz et al., 2019). In this paper, we examine the dynamics of this debate, moving beyond competing ontologies to uncover very different visions of good science, and what it might mean for scientists and plants to stand in good relation. Monica Gagliano, a prominent researcher in the field, argues for a thorough re-evaluation of modern science, calling for a rejection of materialism and hierarchy, as well as illusions of control and objectivity. She sees her research as “a collaborative effort with [her] plant associates” (Gagliano 2018, 33). In this way, she offers a radically new vision of individual researcher-plant relations. But she, and others, go farther, explicitly linking our flawed understanding of plants to our current ecological crisis, advocating for transformed human-plant relationships on a larger scale. In making these claims, a number of women in the field have found it very difficult to obtain funding and professional respect for their work. Drawing on interviews with key scientists involved in the debate as well as books, professional papers and other media, we will look at the contention from some of these researchers that the critiques are essentially antifeminist, and we will highlight the feminist ethics shaping this new field.

Is Non-violent Research Possible? Confronting University Inequalities in a Study of COVID-19 Inequalities
Sarah C Armstrong, University of Glasgow; Lucy Pickering, The University of Glasgow

This paper reflects on our efforts to structure and enact a research process and team that challenged institutional violence within/of the university, while conducting research on institutional violence outside of it. The Scotland in Lockdown study (June-December 2020) explored the impacts of COVID-19 lockdown on already isolated and marginalised people: refugees, sexual violence survivors, disabled people, imprisoned people (<https://scotlandinlockdown.co.uk/>), finding that state systems of support contracted and made people more vulnerable and insecure during the pandemic. It was funded as part of a rapid research programme that sought fast turnaround, high impact work that could inform the emerging response to the pandemic in Scotland. Rapid research in particular discourages attention to the structures of research. In the haste to generate data fast, longstanding questions – about hierarchies in research teams, the use of community partners to supply participants from whom data can be extracted and more – are set aside in the face of situations defined as ‘crisis’. In this paper we reflect on our efforts to resist participation in the structural violence of rapid response research, employing STS scholarship to follow the non-

human actors in this process, namely the university and the pandemic. We also consider how the very discourses of crisis and rapidity central to the structural violence of academic research can be evoked to resist it, for example by allowing much of our work to fall under the radar of otherwise surveillance-heavy bureaucratized, hierarchised university systems.

Sharing Vulnerabilities and an Ethics of Care in Research: Interviewing during Covid19 *Susi Geiger, University College Dublin; MISFIRES Team, University College Dublin*

When we as STS researchers do research, how do we practice care? Care of research participants has infused much of our research practices, both at institutional level through research ethics reviews or boards and at an individual level when we adopt a reflexive or relational ethical position (e.g. Dutton and Dukerich 2006). But how do we – across both of these levels - practice active self-care as researchers within often sensitive or triggering field settings? This paper reports on a longitudinal team research project that involved extensive depth interviewing during the current pandemic on research participants' experiences during Covid19. It reflects on the team's experiences of carrying out this research while sharing deep vulnerabilities with the research participants – namely being caught up in the emotional and mental turmoil of a pandemic, experiencing loss and uncertainty, and being distanced from others. To explore how these vulnerabilities manifested in our research and to infuse our team research with an ethics of (self)care, we engaged in a debriefing process that included free text writing, post-research interviewing and team sensemaking. We utilize Maria Puig de la Bellacasa's ethics of care (e.g. 2012, 2017) and previous writings on vulnerability and reciprocity in the research process (Rhodes and Carlsen 2018) to reflect on this experience and to devise a research-based and institutional agenda for practicing care for the researcher. This self-care agenda will also positively influence the care we show toward our research participants in the often unequal and uncertain world we engage in as researchers.

References: Dutton JE and Dukerich JM (2006) The Relational Foundation of Research: An Underappreciated Dimension of Interesting Research. *The Academy of Management Journal* 49(1). *Academy of Management*, 21–26. Puig de la Bellacasa (2012). 'Nothing comes without its world': thinking with care. *The Sociological Review*, 60(2), 197-216. Puig de La Bellacasa (2017). *Matters of care: Speculative ethics in more than human worlds* (Vol. 41). U of Minnesota Press. Rhodes C and Carlsen A (2018) The teaching of the other: Ethical vulnerability and generous reciprocity in the research process. *Human Relations* 71(10), 1295-1318.

Session Organizer:

Stephen Hughes, Science and Technology Studies, University College London

Discussant:

Christopher Groves, Cardiff University, Cardiff, Wales, United Kingdom

535. STS from the Wounds I

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Participants:

Colonial Science, 'Divide and Conquer' and the 1947 Partition
Sana Saboowala, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign

This paper seeks to illuminate the ways in which the professed depoliticization of science orchestrated violent divisions in South Asia, with a focus on trauma stemming from the 1947 Partition. I use a feminist postcolonial framework to explore the technoscientific colonial practices that created definite borders around identities in South Asia, which were justified by 'objective' science. Drawing from Gyan Pandey's

historiographical work on the construction of communalism in colonial North India, postcolonial STS frameworks, and oral histories from survivors of the 1947 Partition, I trace the ways in which technopolitical practices in colonial India created and exacerbated divisions in society, fueling violence in the region that continues to wound today. Depoliticizing science allowed difference to become politicized via specific nationalist framings, culminating in a geopolitical border and extreme violence. Using a mixed methods approach, I map how the British colonial regime used census and other bureaucratic techniques, like the post-1857 designation of 'martial races,' to scientifically classify and categorize people, creating strict boundaries around concepts that were originally syncretic. Then, I look towards the ways in which differences, often reified through biological concepts like Riskey's anthropometric nasal index, continue to be politicized by various factions, creating conflict, eugenic policy, and oppression today. Finally, I present possibilities for re-politicizing and re-humanizing biological sciences through a focus on individual life histories, embodiment through epigenetics. Ultimately, can we create a feminist technoscience that can heal and learn while acknowledging and understanding the ways in which science has wounded?

Curating and Recrafting as alternative repairs *Fredy Mora Gamez, University of Vienna*

State crimes and forced migration due to war violence and precarity are some of the ongoing entanglements of injustice in the landscape of post-accord Colombia. Such injustice is not diminished by lockdowns, quarantines, or signed peace accords. Within this landscape, governmental reparation and solidarity are still deployed as ambitious yet widely limited techno-political projects reproducing historical and ongoing asymmetric relations of power between states and wounded bodies seeking reparation. Those projects materialise an incapacity of the state to acknowledge the multiplicity of forms of violence and displacement affecting the everyday lives of people on the move and victims of state crimes. Drawing on the repertoire of STS and its experimental intersections with critical migration studies and posthuman understandings of memory, this paper wonders about those sociomaterial worlds exceeding governmental reparation and solidarity, how wounded bodies engage in material transformative practices, and the role of non-humans in the material politics of alternative repair. For doing so, I share my engagement with practices of 'curating mobile memorials' to contest official narratives of the armed conflict and 'recrafting paper' by people on the move finding their ways in the inhospitable streets of Bogotá. Drawing on these ethnographic interfaces, I think-with care about them as alternative repairs, or as worlds for healing and cura-ting wounds by reclaiming justice beyond the boundaries of governmental reparation and solidarity.

Reparation in Worlds After Not-only-human Settler Colonialism *Mara Dicenta, William & Mary*

In this talk, I will explore colonial and racial injustices as they relate to the history of beavers, science, and nature conservation in Tierra del Fuego, the southernmost tip of the Americas. I will show how the introduction of beavers into Tierra del Fuego, along with other human and nonhuman settlers, was motivated by racializing visions that provoked not only severe environmental consequences but also long-term social and political effects. Responding to the ecological effects of such visions, a transnational conservation project is currently trying to eradicate the beavers in order to restore the native ecosystems of Tierra del Fuego. However, and despite the willingness of some indigenous peoples to collaborate in the eradication of beavers, they are often excluded when their goals are not biodiversity conservation but rather land and nature decolonization. With the case of the beavers, I will argue that a just STS requires the ability to let plural understandings of nature, knowledge, and justice coexist. This plurality does not restrict or slow down our capacity to respond to pressing environmental and social

challenges. On the contrary, it multiplies the reparative possibilities that STS has by actively engaging in processes that are already interconnected: intergenerational injustices and global configurations of nature and science. Lastly, with the case of the beavers I will also argue that an STS from the wounds opens up possibilities for engaged methods that go beyond notions of situated knowledges to conceptualize other objectivities that bring ghosts, disavowal, and reparation at the center.

The Masterplan and its Wounds: Wounded history in Rwanda's changing capital *Shakirah Hudani, University of North Carolina, Chapel Hill*

This paper conceptualizes of the new city masterplan of Kigali, Rwanda as a Large Technical System (LTS) (Hughes, 1987) whose overarching knowledge forms and means of spatial production zone out local knowledge and vernacular building. As the post-genocide capital is being reconstructed by way of international expertise and transnational finance, those too poor to remain in the capital are forced to leave to peri-urban and rural areas. How do regimes of master-planning overlap and erase the wounded spaces of vernacular building in the capital? Using qualitative research in Rwanda over a 12 month period (2018-2019), I bring together insights from STS and urban studies and ask how the masterplan creates interlocking terrains of fantasy in wounded, post-genocide, space. I examine the case of building and planning in the capital by looking at informal spaces in Kigali at a time of ongoing expropriation and demolition of informal settlements in the city and argue that the city is a sociotechnical object representative of different periods of national history. Relevant Sources: Hughes, T.P., 1987. The evolution of large technological systems. The social construction of technological systems: New directions in the sociology and history of technology, 82. Jasanoff, S. and Kim, S.H. eds., 2015. Dreamscapes of modernity: Sociotechnical imaginaries and the fabrication of power. University of Chicago Press. Winner, L., 1980. Do artifacts have politics?. *Daedalus*, pp.121-136.

Session Organizer:

Julia Morales Fontanilla, Rutgers University - New Jersey, USA

Chair:

Aadita Chaudhury, York University

536. Governing Environmental Inequalities: Towards a New Research-Action Framework on Agency, Power & Multispecies Justice – II: Energy Governance, Resistance & Conflict

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

Participants:

Indigenous Energy Territories: Infrastructure and Empowerment in the Pacific Northwest *Aaron Gregory, University of California at Berkeley*

Renewable energy infrastructures are increasingly developed by Indigenous communities seeking to decolonize and decarbonize tribal lands frequently torn asunder through processes of intensive energy production and resource extraction. These projects often emerge to displace or augment existing energy architectures controlled by state, private and multinational actors, championed to expand our range of solutions to climate change, environmental degradation and the ongoing colonization of Indigenous lands. The resulting proliferation of Indigenous Energy Territories — regions shaped through renewable energy systems governed by Indigenous communities — attends to the decolonizing and decarbonizing potential of infrastructure to accomplish these interrelated goals. Through a 'methods assemblage' approach to Indigenous STS drawing upon insights gleaned through related research in the Pacific Northwest, this paper demonstrates infrastructure as a new terrain of

environmental governance shaped through articulations between Native knowledge, expertise and novel approaches of techno-scientific management. It explores the deliberative processes of design and governance drawn together to manage these renewable energy systems, and how new forms of social and territorial belonging are produced through community connectivities to networked infrastructure.

Divisible Governance: making gas-fired futures inevitable amid climate collapse *Kirsty Howey, University of Sydney; Timothy Neale, Deakin University*

This paper examines how new fossil fuel projects are entrenched today, despite the wide acceptance that they will accelerate ecological collapse caused by climate change, and the promise of alternative renewable energy sources that should render such projects obsolete. Using a combination of legal/policy analysis and interviews, we analyse reforms to regulate a proposed new shale gas industry in the hot (and heating) remote Northern Territory of Australia, using "fracking" techniques. The paper introduces the concept of "divisible governance" - produced through the technical manoeuvres of risk fragmentation, temporal fragmentation, and jurisdictional fragmentation. Divisible governance is coproduced (Jasanoff, 2004) by these time-honoured legal-scientific practices to not only entrench new fossil fuel projects, but also to sustain ignorance about the nature and extent of their risks. Divisible environmental governance is thus deceptive governance, despite its central claim of achieving transparency and accountability. S. Jasanoff (2004). *States of Knowledge: The Co-production of Science and the Social Order*. Routledge.

Contested socio-environmental imaginaries in times of hydro-extractivism in Costa Rica *Francesc Rodriguez, Brandenburg University of Technology*

In the context of hydro-extractive industry development in Costa Rica, a wave of applications for private concessions to build run-of-the-river dams has swept over the country during the last decade. These hydroelectric project plans have caused concern among residents adjacent to the targeted rivers to the extent that a socio-environmental conflict has erupted in several communities of the southern Pacific side of the country. Using a multi-sited ethnographic approach, in this article, I elucidate the resistance of local people to these plans with a focus on the contestation to the Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA) reports of two hydroelectric project plans. By showing the underlying socio-environmental imaginaries and ontologies that underpin the conflict over dam development, my article shows the different ontologies of water and rivers, providing insights into the existing gap between institutionalized and noninstitutionalized ways of knowing about water under the development model of hydro-extractivism.

Emergence of an hydroelectric turbine, repairs and maintenance in Puerto Edén, Magallanes Region, Chile *Cristian Valenzuela Calderon, Universidad Alberto Hurtado; Cecilia Ibarra, Universidad de Chile*

Based on the case study of the emergence of a mini hydroelectric power station in the remote town of Puerto Edén, in the South of Chile, we reflect on the discontinuities and transformations of electricity supply processes. Infrastructures are assemblages that do not have the characteristics of being stable with fully defined limits, but are updated through material and discursive rearrangements (Ureta, 2017; Star and Ruhleder, 1996). Updates can be obtained through the actions of repairing and maintaining infrastructures (Henke, 2019). During the 90's, the Eden mini hydroelectric plant emerged as a community option (in a turbine committee) and through the supply of materials, people and knowledge in a public-private partnership. When the energy supply emerged through an hydroelectric turbine in Eden, a material scenario was produced and interacted with the water environment. Those in charge of maintaining and repairing this

infrastructure appeared in the locality as translators (Callon, 1995) of its operation. However, the lack of capacities of the maintainers to solve common power supply problems demanded from the Edenina community to solve turbine failures. This situation caused the community to get involved in the repairs of an environmental infrastructure, in which they must configure narratives and interventions in the water and electricity flows. Puerto Eden's energy trajectory is discontinuous, and to understand its effects, it is of utmost importance to interrogate memory, which, in this case, produces learning about the ways of assembling a built environment with its hydric landscapes.

Session Organizer:

William San Martin, Worcester Polytechnic Institute (WPI)

Chair:

William San Martin, Worcester Polytechnic Institute (WPI)

Discussant:

Martín Fonck, Rachel Carson Center for Environment and Society

537. Inclusion and Its Consequences: The Politics of Diversity and Recognition in Health Data Projects - III

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Engaging with the 4S 2021 conference theme, this panel explores the practices and consequences of data inclusion and exclusion in unequal worlds. We welcome empirical and conceptual papers examining health data projects of various scales, that consider some of the following questions: What are the various promises of diversity linked to data projects and how do these promises shape inclusion and exclusion practices, efforts, and outcomes? What are the tradeoffs and dilemmas inherent in and arising from narratives and practices of inclusion in health data projects? What are the drivers of activism around inclusion in health data and, alternatively, what drives resistance? How do current struggles for inclusion in health data today differ from demands for inclusion in the past? What sorts of visibilities and erasures might inclusion and exclusion in health data produce? This panel invites papers examining data assemblages and what it means to be counted (or not) in health data, to whom, and for what ends. Papers might address, for example, the inclusion or exclusion of various identifiers and statuses in state surveillance systems, the participation or refusal of communities in health data repositories, interrogations of public and private institutions that seek to obscure data collection, and erasures and ethical challenges that arise as data emerge from and circulate across geographic scales from the local to the transnational.

Participants:

Base Pairs and Bases for Health Disparities: Tracing Population Stratification in Genetic Epidemiology *Carolina Mayes, UC San Diego*

Research into the genetic contributions to common and chronic diseases has long struggled with the complex diagnostics and biological nature of these illnesses, and has intersected for many decades with epidemiological expertise. Within the subfield of genetic epidemiology, methods including linkage analysis and linkage disequilibrium were revolutionized during the completion of the Human Genome Project, as a previously favored form of genetic variation, restriction fragment length polymorphisms, was displaced by the more common single nucleotide polymorphisms (SNPs). SNP-based methodologies rapidly shifted disease research from pedigree-based linkage studies to population-based association studies, including the now mainstay method of genome-wide association studies (GWAS). Using a text-based analysis of textbooks and published research, I trace the methodology of population analysis in genetic epidemiology from its parentage in population genetics, and consider how reliance on statistical parameters to define the population object continues to pose uncertainties for genomic population health projects today. I argue that the statistical grounding of the genetic population concept has produced

ambiguity about the meaning of “population” across the history of human genetics as a field, which has helped keep genetic population concepts in discursive lockstep with racial categories continuing into the present. Finally, I suggest that the reliance on statistical parameters for population boundaries has bearing on the clinical translation of genomics in the present. Genomic and precision medicine initiatives like the federal All of Us initiative must interface between genetically determined population boundaries, their own commitments to health disparities research, and the social and medical salience of race.

Of Transformative Promises and Future-making : Digital Health Initiatives in India *Nishtha Bharti, Indian Institute of Technology, New Delhi*

Through my paper, I will foreground the Indian government's value-laden choices and commitments that pervade the legislative arena pertaining to data-based, artificial intelligence-driven, digital health initiatives. I will strive to argue that an overtone of generic superfluity around technological interventions is a recurring feature in the policy pronouncements of the Government of India, and indicates a practise of ‘future-making’ that not only shapes the direction and governance of innovation but more importantly, the identification of problems that actually need concerted intervention of public and private actors. An instantiation of this is the unrelenting push for data-driven health projects, such as through the National Health Policy (2017), National Health Stack (2018), National Digital Health Blueprint (2019) and the National Digital Health Mission (2020). These policies are an exercise in grandstanding - offering to transform the healthcare ecosystem in India through an expansive health data infrastructure and analytics, ostensibly to remove all roadblocks in the path of acquiring equity and inclusivity. Yet at the same time, they decidedly steer away from a reflexive assessment of the fact that certain cohorts are systemically excluded from the limited datasets upon which the entire edifice of digital health projects is envisioned. These policy documents also do not acknowledge the possibility that the social dynamics that prevent marginalised patient groups from accessing healthcare in the first place will replicate onto digital data infrastructures, undermining the potential of digital health initiatives to act as a silver bullet that can alleviate the persistent healthcare challenges in India. I would endeavour to highlight that such a move conceals the deliberate policy silences around the pressing needs of an unequal socio-political order and at the same time, occludes any accountability from addressing those needs and issues.

Data Activism During the Pandemic: Demanding, Contesting or Producing Race-based COVID-19 Data. *Loes Knaapen, Université d'Ottawa*

Daily ‘Covid counts’ have been central to the narrative, governance and experience of COVID-19, as governments rely on ‘the numbers’ to justify their (lack of) response to the pandemic. The public does not simply accept or reject such numbers, they actively contest what is counted by official statistics and criticized what goes unmeasured. In North America, the collection of ‘race-based’ COVID-19 data – and lack thereof – has been particularly contested by health professionals, academics, journalists and activists. Many are in favor of collecting race-based data, declaring that making racial inequalities in health visible is “the first step” in tackling them. Others are critical of how this data is to be collected, including challenges before (e.g. how to classify race), during (e.g. missing data) and after collection (e.g. how to interpret and use such data). Those opposing race-based COVID-19 data are less visible, but some warn surveillance of Black communities is likely to result in state sponsored violence, not care. Drawing on the sociology of quantification and critical data studies, this paper will analyze the numerous public contestations over race-based COVID-19 data. Based on a content analysis of popular media, formal reports, and selective websites/social media, I will

examine and contrast public data activism in Canada and the USA. In the latter, a large public/private open-source data-making collective has been established (COVID racial data tracker) to collect, analyze and publish available data. In Canada, public pressures have resulted in public and governmental institutions starting to produce race-based COVID-19 data.

The Rise of Diversity and Population Terminology in Biomedical Research *Brandon Kramer, University of Virginia; Catherine Lee, Rutgers University*

While existing research on race and affirmative action have detailed the growth of diversity projects in education and employment that obfuscate the language of race and racism, the field of science & technology studies have documented scientists persistent attempts to molecularize race in biomedical research. In this paper, we employ computational text analysis to examine quantitative trends in the use of diversity terms, OMB/Census terms, and other population labels in a sample of 2.6+ million biomedical abstracts spanning the last 30 years. These analyses demonstrate that while racial, ethnic, and OMB/Census terms have mostly stagnated during the past 15 years, the use of “diversity” continues to rise, suggesting that biomedical researchers increasingly use a different grammar to construct population differences. We also observe that some population labels have grown dramatically with specific kinds of population terms outpacing others. Most notably, we find that the use of national and continental terms rose exponentially while terms like race and OMB/Census labels have actually dropped over the past decade. Together, our work points to a potential shift in the way that biomedical researchers enact population distinctions, relying more on biogeographical labels rather than racial or ethnic classifiers. Overall, this work not only informs STS and bioethics scholars’ research on the politics of diversity in biomedical research, but also shares a novel set of methodological tools, including open source software and a new public dataset, to research this topic.

Session Organizers:

Janet K. Shim, University of California, San Francisco
Sandra Soo-Jin Lee, Columbia University

538. Author-Meets-Critics: Anaesthetics of Existence and Beautyscapes

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

This author-meets-critics panel engages with two recent books on embodied experience and technologies of the self. Cressida Heyes’ *Anaesthetics of Existence* argues that “experience” as a social and political category must have its own constitutive exclusions. Her chapters examine why liminal events—the rape of unconscious victims, the emptiness of evening drinking, and giving birth—have been excluded from experience, and how technologies in media, management, and medicine compel or enable us to step outside ourselves. *Beautyscapes*, by contrast, looks at a particular site of embodied change: international medical travel for cosmetic surgeries. It traces the relationships between different agents in the structures that enable it, while offering illustrative narratives based on rich ethnographic research. Heyes and Jones are previous collaborators who find exciting and novel connections between their very different work as a philosopher and sociologist of culture, respectively. Both books seek to understand the material conditions of lived experience, moving between the larger frames of institutionalized technologies (obstetrics or surgery; digital images; anaesthesia) to personal narrative, and back again. Both have an intersectional feminist method, and both examine crossing between and liminality—the movement from home country to surgical site and holiday destination, or from surgical before to after; as well as from working self to leisure self, or from pregnant to parent. These themes are elaborated by two of our long-time junior collaborators: J. R. Latham connects this scholarship to critiques of medicine within trans studies, and Catherine Clune-Taylor comments on how racial inequities in healthcare constrain narratives of self.

Participants:

After Anaesthetics: The Politics of Refusal *Cressida J. Heyes, University of Alberta - Edmonton*

My book *Anaesthetics of Existence* concludes with the suggestion that its examination of anaesthetic time, “checking out,” and complicating understandings of agency implicated with neoliberal norms could feed into a “politics of refusal.” This idea has been articulated by various thinkers—from Indigenous political theorists such as Audra Simpson or Glen Coulthard who refuse the cooptations of settler sovereignty, to those in the “Slow” movement who politicize the demand to rush, to antiwork theorists sceptical that freedom can be found in waged labour and the ethic of productivity. In this presentation I want to extend this idea, showing how and why it was the book’s concluding note, but also connecting this mode of thinking to the complex debates about freedom and choice under conditions of constraint that shape decisions about body technologies. *Beautyscapes* shows how seemingly individual decisions to travel for cosmetic surgery are caught up in chains of transnational actors. As the book shows, the relations between these actors are often represented through moralizing, judgmental, or individualizing frames that are somewhat distant from both the personal acts of agency, self-doubt, or ambivalence that characterize the decision to have a surgery, and the large political analyses of the world that makes them possible. Thus both books—and both authors—are trying to find spaces in which the complexity of local agency can be honoured, while the reality of political constraints are not dismissed.

Global Bodies: Aesthetics, Anaesthetics and Being Elsewhere *Meredith Jones, Brunel University London*

This paper introduces my book (with Ruth Holliday and David Bell) *Beautyscapes: Mapping Cosmetic Surgery Tourism* (MUP, 2020). After describing what cosmetic surgery tourism is I debunk some of the common fallacies around the practice, such as the beliefs that it is more dangerous than cosmetic surgery at home, and that people who seek it are vain and foolish. I argue that cosmetic surgery abroad is a logical response to the pressures of living within neoliberal regimes wherein bodies and their aesthetics constitute capital. I link this notion of bodily beauty as real capital to processes of transformation under anaesthetic and to changes that are occur in other places-- 'elsewhere'--and thus make connections with Heyes' book. This paper asks 'what is it to go into the unknown, embrace unknown risks, and return transformed?'

Experiencing Experience: Re-turning to the Gender Clinic *J. R. Latham, Deakin University*

How do medical processes take account of “experience” and its own constitutive exclusions in the context of changing sex? Long has it been argued by trans scholars that medicine misunderstands “the complexities and ambiguities of [trans people’s] lived experience” (Stone, 1991), yet medical rhetoric and practices continue to ignore – or make absent – constitutive elements of trans people’s subjectivity, especially related to sexuality. Inspired by the oeuvre of Heyes and Jones, I consider how medical practices and practitioners might better make space for the complexities and ambiguities of the diverse material and political conditions trans people live under, and hence improve quality of patient care and accessibility to medical services. Engaging analysis of institutionalized technologies and personal narratives, I think through how trans people’s own accounts of crossing between and liminality are both made absent and might be made present in current political climates of seeking transgender medical interventions, and to what effects.

Session Organizer:

Cressida J. Heyes, University of Alberta - Edmonton

Chair:

Bronwyn Wilson, The University Of Melbourne

Discussant:

Catherine Clune-Taylor, Princeton University

539. Challenges of -and Opportunities for- STS Undergraduate Programs, Teaching and Education - II

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Whether one characterises STS as an interdisciplinary field of inquiry, a full-fledge discipline, or otherwise, it is a body of knowledges and academic practices with its own core ideas, concepts, texts, journals, and professional associations. Yet education in STS is much less standardized than in other established fields and disciplines. While STS graduate programs exist in various forms and under various titles almost globally, undergraduate programs are much less common. Furthermore, given their interdisciplinarity, STS undergraduate programs face distinct sets of pedagogical and institutional challenges in terms of getting them established, as well as operating and maintaining them. At the same time, STS undergraduate programs are uniquely positioned to offer students with aspirations both within and outside the field, a set of theories, practices and methods that equip them to understand and address problems of inequality and uncertainty within our communities, institutions, and world. We invite papers that reflect on the pedagogical and institutional dynamics of teaching STS and developing STS programs at the undergraduate level. Submissions can be connected -but are not limited- to: •Undergraduate awareness of and general visibility of STS as a field •Impacts of disciplinary dynamics within STS on education and programing •Interdisciplinary education •Relationships with natural science programs, students, and faculty (i.e. Science Wars in education, the place of STS in mainstream STEM education) •Program development: majors, minors, core courses and electives •Institutional dynamics of program development •Appropriate modes of assessment •Researching STS pedagogy •Teaching the STS canon – best practices Potential topics include: STS undergraduate teaching, pedagogy, STS disciplinary development Jill Lazenby, York University, Toronto Conor Douglas, York University Vera Pavri, York University

Participants:

Joys and Challenges of Teaching STS to Career-Focused STEM Students *Christine Keiner*

Rochester Institute of Technology is a private university that serves approximately 15,700 undergraduates and 2,900 graduate students. Women constitute 35% of the total student body, and RIT achieved R2 status in 2019. The most popular majors encompass engineering and computer science, though the number of undergraduate degree programs in the College of Liberal Arts has grown over the past decade. The Science, Technology, and Society Department, however, still lacks an undergraduate degree. The STS faculty are an interdisciplinary group, and have delivered general-education courses since the 1980s, including a few required courses for environmental science majors. While the administration rejected our proposal for an Environmental Studies degree, we now have a preliminary proposal for a major in Science, Technology, and Society under consideration by the provost's office. We believe the proposal makes a strong case for providing more well-rounded STEM educational initiatives, especially by emphasizing that STEM practitioners need interdisciplinary knowledge from the humanities and social sciences to ensure that their work does not perpetuate injustice. In this presentation I will draw upon my own experiences and those of my colleagues to address opportunities for and challenges of teaching science and technology studies at a highly career-focused STEM institution that focuses on creativity and innovation primarily via the intersectional lenses of technology, art, and design.

Science and the Paranormal in the STS Classroom *Darby Orcutt*, NC State University

Gallup polls consistently show that three-quarters of Americans hold one or more “paranormal” beliefs. If paranormal ideas are normal, why are they largely dismissed in our cultural practices

of science? For three semesters now, I've taught a course on science and the paranormal that examines this cultural, philosophical, and historical divide, and is unafraid to ask students to assess the best scientific evidence in support of Sasquatch hypotheses and Parapsychology. Harnessing students' strong curiosity about paranormal topics, we use these “fringe” fields as a lens into how science works in the real world, including looking at how different disciplines define and scope evidence, the role of scientific models in posing research questions, statistical reasoning, issues of reproducibility, concepts of scale and measurement, and the use of instrumentation. Alongside this, we examine broader cultural views of science and their impacts, including the history of conflicts between science and religion/belief, the development of scientific disciplines, media coverage of science and the paranormal, citizen science, relations with indigenous communities, the concept of progress in science, hoaxes and hoax hypotheses, and the capital-S Sceptical movement. Students engage in hands-on learning and reflection, for example: conducting their own psi experiments and building their own EMF (electromagnetic frequency) meters. Students in the course are encouraged to critically “think and do,” and ultimately to develop their own embodied sense of how to conduct scientific inquiry and situate scientific thinking within society and life.

STS Student as a Misunderstanding Expert in a Field of Competing Disciplines and Expert Cultures *Marko Zivkovic*, University of Alberta

This paper will explore some strategies for organizing an undergraduate STS curriculum around the idea that students should, among other things, become (budding) experts in misunderstandings among disciplinary and expert cultures. Experts in today's world have to collaborate, but they often have trouble communicating among themselves. Interdisciplinarity is easy to talk about but hard to practice. A good translator among disciplinary/expert cultures then has to have what Collins and Evans called “interactional expertise” in all the fields they translate between. How then to teach STS students to be good at quickly “cracking” scientific or expert cultures to the point of being able to mediate their mutual misunderstandings? Building on the author's insights from studying the “dialogue of the deaf” between artists and neuroscientists and running the Fieldschool for Ethnographic Sensibility that uses arts training to teach Holmesian detection skills for ethnographic research, a pedagogy will be proposed that relies on sensitivity to metaphors and what Myers and Dumit call “haptic creativity.” The idea is that attention to verbal and embodied metaphors, the kinds of “kinesthetic imagination” Myers described in *Rendering Life Molecular*, is a “royal road” into cracking epistemic cultures and thus being to mediate among them. The paper will propose that this skill of acrobatically jumping in and out of disciplinary worlds that is a prerequisite for becoming an expert in misunderstanding among them is best taught by focusing on the modes of flexible inquiry shared among arts and sciences.

Session Organizers:

Conor Douglas, York University

Vera Pavri, York University

Jill Lazenby, York University, Toronto

Chair:

Jill Lazenby, York University, Toronto

Discussant:

Vera Pavri, York University

540. Methodologies without walls: Radical reimagining of hierarchies in scientific research and practice on health inequities

3:00 to 4:40 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

This panel investigates the various ways in which methods and

methodologies used in social science and biomedical research re-constitute and perpetuate racial injustices. The papers in the panel seek to recognize and challenge hegemonic structures that undergird knowledge production in medicine, scientific methodologies, media, and community-academic relationships. Based on multi-disciplinary social science research that centers on Black and African American communities, this panel highlights how our own research is embedded within and constrained by methodological hierarchies, which are often rooted in structural racism and other systems of oppression. We challenge these embedded hierarchies by formulating alternative, seemingly radical but entirely pragmatic ways forward through research practices that draw upon community-partnered participatory research and intersectional analysis. We also consider how these embedded hierarchies are reinforced through medical knowledge and everyday interaction with health care professionals. We interrogate ways in which these hegemonic structures shape what we imagine, know, and make real while generating knowledge about health inequities. This panel contributes to STS by going beyond how this problem has been typically imagined and addressed. We critically examine research assumptions that health inequities can be solved by providing more resources and access to services or by eliminating discriminatory biases without unrooting the hierarchies or dismantling institutional structures racism. The papers in this panel offer a deeper analysis by re-centering and exposing the very methodological frameworks we work from, which we argue perpetuates the epistemological boundaries and reproduction of health inequities.

Participants:

A Case-Study in the Recent Contextual History of Community-Partnered Participatory Research *Roberto Vargas, Charles R. Drew University of Medicine and Science; Felicia Jones, Healthy African American Families*

This paper provides a contextual history of community academic partnerships in research that demonstrate recent paradigm shifts in health research practices, products, and policies. To the extent that they will represent a passing trend or a sustained paradigm shift remains to be seen. Using case studies, we describe sentinel benchmarks in the transition of community “based” to “partnered” research frameworks in the first two decades of the 21st century. This includes individual and institutional formal research partnerships, grant funding, peer reviewed products, training programs, and academic institutional policies. We describe these internal structures and processes in the context of the external sociopolitical environment of federal and foundation research policy changes that explicitly supported these models. Cases are derived from community-partnered participatory research projects in depression, kidney disease, and cancer and demonstrate the partnered framework’s approach to inclusion from hypothesis development, study design, the conduct of research, analysis, and interpretation of results. The sociopolitical environment examples include the National Institutes of Health’s transition of the National Center for Research Resources to the National Center for Advancing Translational Sciences and the research funding priorities of major foundations such as the Robert Wood Johnson Foundation. Through these case studies, we provide examples of community-partnered participatory research including their structures and process and the external factors that run concurrent to them. These described models provide context to inform policies to promote the sustainability and evolution of these types of community partnerships in research.

Methodologies of epistemic (in)justice: Reclaiming the power of ‘community’ in community-partnered participatory research on health inequities *Olga Solomon, University of Southern California; Aziza Lucas Wright, Charles Drew University of Medicine and Science; South Central Prevention Coalition*

The COVID-19 pandemic has revealed the devastating consequences of disinvestment in the health of African Americans in the U.S. The pandemic is forcing a radical reexamination of methods and assumptions that have been

utilized in the knowledge production on ‘health disparities’ in African American communities; and a realization that the research enterprise has played a major role in perpetuating inequity and epistemic injustice in healthcare by excluding African American communities from major research and policy decisions impacting their health. While some methodological approaches have mostly obscured the underlying roots of differences in health outcomes, others have been uniquely equipped to reveal them. The Community-Partnered Participatory Research (CPPR) model has been a major advancement in research on health inequity over the past two and a half decades. Although it has been promoted by Clinical and Translational Science Awards (CTSA) programs at research universities as a preferred community engagement model, the truly equal partnerships of community and academia have been rare. CPPR presents unique challenges to community-academic partnerships because it calls for a hierarchical equity in funding, research strategy decisions, and other areas that academic researchers assume to be under their unquestioned jurisdiction. Thus, it forces a re-examination of relationships and re-negotiation of power, positionalities, identities, roles, and responsibilities of community and academic collaborators that are radically different from more traditional ‘community-based’ models. We discuss the seemingly paradoxical but unsurprising situations when CPPR – guided projects continue to be afflicted by the community-academia power inequity that the model has been seeking to alleviate.

Race and the Science of “Vaccine Hesitancy” *Kristin Bumiller, Department of Political Science*

This paper offers a critique of how epidemiologists study vaccine hesitancy and the assumptions this field makes about medically underserved community members. While enormous attention is given to conspiracy theories as the primary cause of vaccine hesitancy, researchers often fail to fully appreciate the impact of economic inequalities or racial discrimination on vaccine skepticism. Scientific studies of vaccine hesitancy often employ misconceptions about group identity and unfounded speculations about reasons for “non-compliance.” New approaches to public health research are needed to show how reluctance to vaccinate stems from distrust which often emerges from personal interactions with health professionals. Only by taking a deeper look at the impact of a long history of insensitive, discriminatory, and inadequate medical treatment can researchers appreciate why some communities are more resistant to vaccination and/or responding to lack of access. Conventional methodologies employed by epidemiologists examine the factors influencing individuals’ health care choices, rather than considering how systematic discrimination delegitimizes public health initiatives. In the context of the pandemic, there is a vital need for a paradigm shift in how researchers view vaccine skepticism, by moving away from approaches which assume the problem lies with aberrant individuals easily swayed by misinformation to examining how communities interact with medical professionals. This raises larger questions for STS about how structural racism continues to erode the legitimacy of public health systems and how community “partnered” research methodologies offer a better approach to understand vaccine choices.

Challenging Hegemonic Assumptions in Autism Disparities Research *Jennifer S Singh, Georgia Institute of Technology*

This paper critically examines the hegemonic assumptions built into research designed to explain the differences in autism diagnosis, treatment, and services based on race and social class. In 2016, I started an ethnography of autism services experienced by Black caregivers of children with autism, which consisted of over 50 interviews and 250 hours of observation in an autism clinic that serves primarily low-income and racial and ethnic minority children. Early on, I began to question many research assumptions that were explaining autism service disparities after hearing the lived experiences of Black caregivers. This

challenged me to examine autism services inequities through an intersectional lens that considers interlocking ideological, economic, and political systems of oppression. In this analysis, I identify hegemonic assumptions that shape how current knowledge of autism service inequalities are understood, including 1) the assumptions built into the notion of “culture” to explain racial differences in diagnosis; 2) the assumptions of “family” that do not consider different family structures outside of normative frameworks; and 3) the assumptions of “care,” which, in the neoliberal age, focus on individualized approaches to seeking and accessing autism services. I argue that these underlying assumptions not only shape epistemological injustices in understanding autism service inequities but also obscure, as evidence from the experiences of Black female caregivers, the various institutional structures that shape access to autism services. This paper contributes to the field of STS by examining the taken for granted epistemological frameworks of health disparities research that unwittingly reinforce autism service inequalities.

Session Organizers:

Jennifer S Singh, Georgia Institute of Technology
Aziza Lucas Wright, Charles Drew University of Medicine and Science; South Central Prevention Coalition

Chair:

Olga Solomon, University of Southern California

Discussant:

Keith Norris, UCLA, David Geffen School of Medicine, UCLA Division of General Internal Medicine and Health Service

541. Boxes as Method

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

This Meetup will experiment with the study of boxes in their broadest scope and scale. We invite participants to rethink scholarly formats by examining boxes and box practices – epistemic, ontic, material, physical, digital. Points of departure will include “Boxes. A Field Guide”(Mattering Press 2020), but also the work by scholars who have long been grappling with how the world is boxed up and how it could be otherwise. In her 1986 essay “The carrier bag theory of fiction”, Ursula LeGuin proposes the container as hero and positions science fiction as recipient and transformative realism for a strange reality. At the Meetup we will discuss box practices as modes of story-ing and box studies as means to make space for a generative critique of western epistemologies and their orderings. After a few short introductory statements we will open up for conversations on boxes as diffractive method. For instance, a focus on boxes may help us cut pathways through the underwood of empirical materials, examine overlooked orderings, and probe possible abductions of the boxes we live and write by. Discussant: Helen Verran.

Session Organizer:

Susanne Bauer, University of Oslo

Chair:

Martina Schlünder, MPIWG

542. Politics of data and quantification as modes of governing (Part 2)

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 10

Techniques and technology have played a major role in the studies of governance ever since the pioneering works of Michel Foucault. Performativity of classification, quantification, and datafication is nowadays a central tenet of a number of fields. STS has showed how politics play out on the level of producing scientific knowledge, governmentality studies have studied the diverse locations of governing, and recent work in critical data studies, data activism, and data justice has shown the political and normative variability of data practices. In addition to this theoretical expansion, material proliferation of digital data forces more practitioners than ever to engage with the politics of data. They must negotiate the competing political pressures of participating in, shaping, and

sometimes rejecting digital assemblages. Keeping good relations between citizens and data practitioners invites us to address the politics of data and its devices and techniques as a mode of governance. How do practitioners understand and navigate the political dilemmas of contemporary data practices? How do politics unfold, become visible, or remain invisible for practitioners? How are these dilemmas materialized in work, tools, and systems? How should we as researchers relate to such dilemmas? How does, if at all, recent attention to ethics and justice influence practitioner perceptions of data politics? The panel tries to expand STS discussion on data practices by inviting submissions that draw from sociology, political science, and media and communications. The panel welcomes especially empirical papers, but is also open to conceptual, theoretical, and philosophical papers that address data politics.

Participants:

Cracks in data solidarity? Politics of “secondary use” of health register data in Finland *Ilpo Helén, University of Eastern Finland*

The Nordic welfare states have often been claimed to be based on widespread generalized trust among people and the ethos of solidarity. These features have also facilitated the evolution of ‘data solidarity’ that allows extensive and routinized collection of personal data in national repositories and use of that data for the provision of healthcare and social benefits to the citizens, and for research supporting the functioning of the welfare state. Recently, a new context for ‘data solidarity’ has emerged, as advocacy for more intense and expanded data sourcing from the national population, healthcare, and social service registers has grown stronger in the Nordic countries. The advocates have claimed that more intense data sourcing from the national give an immense boost to innovative business in domestic high-tech ‘health sector’. According to them, more ‘interoperable’ and easily accessible national databases would attract outside users, especially big transnational pharmaceutical and ICT enterprises, to collaborate with local companies and research institutions. In my paper, I analyse the promotion of expansion of the ‘secondary use’ of healthcare and social service data in Finland in the 2010s as an example of the Nordic innovation policy that aims at connecting national health-related data repositories to global health data economy. I focus my analysis on is reshaping of the Nordic ‘data solidarity’, as the new data policy rationale embraces widespread trust and willingness in data sourcing in the Nordic countries, and simultaneously, subverts them.

Governing Vulnerable Pregnancy *Hugo Peeters, Erasmus University Rotterdam*

This study draws on actor-network theory to investigate how ‘vulnerable pregnancy’ is constituted as an object of governance through four new screening instruments. Between 2008 and 2018 eight new prenatal screening instruments for detecting psychosocial risk-factors of adverse pregnancy were tested out in the Netherlands, some of which are now being used by practicing midwives. By screening pregnant women for factors like mental health, income, stress, substance abuse or social relations, these instruments aim to detect the new classification of ‘vulnerable pregnancy’: pregnancies in which an accumulation of psychosocial risk-factors puts unborn children at an increased risk of developing various problems later in life. In the Netherlands development of psychosocial screening instruments accelerated in response to alarming rates of birth complications, but the growing concern with psychosocial screening of pregnancy reflects somewhat of an international trend. Policy actors in the United Kingdom, Australia, the United States and many other countries have come to see psychosocial screening as a cost-effective instrument for improving health, creating equality and decreasing crime levels amongst future populations. Our study zooms in on the Dutch context to follow the performance of vulnerable pregnancy in realtime, as actors adjust to, tinker with and negotiate the new networks of interdependencies taking shape between them. Through an

ethnographic case study we trace how four psychosocial screening and intervention instruments mediate interdependencies between the researchers developing the instrument, practicing midwives and pregnant women classified as vulnerable.

Quantifying Ability, Shaping Ordinal Citizens: Assembling Disability Data in India *Kim Fernandes, University of Pennsylvania*

Who comes to be counted as disabled, and under what circumstances? What are the implications of obtaining identity documentation that confirms one's everyday experiences of disability? In India, disability is measured and certified with a particular focus on the percentage or degree to which a person is considered 'disabled enough' to be officially counted as disabled. Certifying disability is a significant but paradoxical citizenship-making process, since it institutes an ordinal citizenship of sorts, affirming belonging not as a binary but through degrees. This certification occurs through the disability certificate and its recent successor, the digital Unique Disability ID (UDID), both government-issued documents that work to make the body legible through subjective, often competing notions of ability. Through attention to the processes that shape the quantification of ability, this paper explores the political and epistemological contexts within which numbers are produced and people's abilities are categorized as data. By asking and seeking to understand what it means to "count" and be counted by the state as disabled, this paper discusses the biological production of politics, rights and citizenship. To do so, it draws upon a combination of virtual ethnographic fieldwork, interviews and archival work, wherein certification is examined as a process of establishing, controlling and re-defining the margins of the state. Finally, in its consideration of how disabled bodies are bounded and made legible to the state in India, this paper will also examine the ways in which data infrastructures intersect with notions of what a body can do.

The Datafication Of Abortion Debates In Ecuador: A "Scientific" Clash Between Pro-choice And Pro-life Groups *Maria Elissa Torres Carrasco, Kaleidos Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography*

Drawing on digital archives from eleven debates over the decriminalization of abortion in Ecuador's National Assembly in 2019, this paper illustrates the production and manipulative use of scientific discourses. By examining the "facts" brought to the fore during the debates, I argue that both pro-choice and pro-life groups construct their political discourses on the issue of abortion when the pregnancy is caused by rape, around their own generated data or partial scientific facts. In a context where pro-choice groups were known for their scientific backing in legislative debates, it is a novelty to find pro-life groups using similar strategic argumentative strategies. This shift to what I understand as a "datafied discourse" of abortion—a highly polemic and sensitive subject in a mostly catholic country—reflects a shift towards science and academia and away from morality and religion. In conversation with STS scholarship on technopolitics, I follow how pro-life policy makers generate scientific statements to manipulate public opinion while pro-choice policy makers try to expose the "real" facts in a country with no official data on abortions as they remain illegal. Even though many ecuadorians recognize (illegal) abortions as a public health issue, the need to produce and use "scientific" findings in the legislative arena is a new occurrence. I am particularly interested in documenting these opposing and disputed scientific claims in an effort to better understand how science moves from academia to the political arena and through ecuadorian society at large.

Data Methods and Knowledge Controversy in the Evolution of China's Family Planning Policy *Zhicong Shang, University of Chinese Academy of Sciences*

This paper uses archival literature survey and visiting research to study the use and influence of data science in the formulation of China's family planning policy since the 1980s. The study found that in the 1980s, when the Chinese government formulated its family planning policy, there were three kinds of competing knowledge proposal. Among them, Jian Song used computer to simulate population growth according to population cybernetics. Although population cybernetics has some defects in ignoring people's various needs, its precise theoretical calculation has the upper hand. Accurate data are beginning to become an important consideration in government policy making. Since 2011, in the process of formulating a new family planning policy in China, there has been fierce competition for two kinds of knowledge proposal, represented by Zhenwu Zhai and Guangzhou Wang, based on the precise measurement of the fertility will of women and the population growth rate in China. Driven by academia and the public, the China government launched a parallel study of two research groups in 2015, conducting a large-scale supplementary population survey, which gradually converted the data and ultimately supported the second-child policy. In the process of family planning policy formulation and implementation, the refinement of data methods has gradually been recognized by the Chinese government and the public, and has become an indispensable and necessary factor in policy making. Since 1980's, data science and its fine requirements have become a factor of Chinese civic epistemology.

Session Organizer:

Ville Aula, London School Of Economics & Political Science

543. Re-thinking 4S Conference Format Meet-Up

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 11

This meet-up provides a space for collectively discussing how to re-think the conference format of our 4S annual meetings. Preliminary work has been advanced by a working committee within 4S council, but we would like to create a discussion open to all 4S members to re-think how we envision the organizing of annual conferences going forward. We intend for this open discussion to bring to the fore issues of climate change, underrepresentation, financial burden, care and academic compatibility, accessibility, among other issues we are currently considering. We will present preliminary findings but would hope to amplify the debate and find common paths going forward. All are welcome.

Session Organizers:

Duygu Kasdogan, İzmir Katip Çelebi University

Angela Okune, University of California - Irvine

Chair:

Maka Suarez, Kaleidos - Center for Interdisciplinary Ethnography

544. STS Food & Agriculture Network (STSFAN) Meetup

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

The STS Food & Agriculture Network (STSFAN) was born out of a set of sessions organized by the AFTeR project (a California-based Agri-Food Technology Research Collaboration) at the 2019 4S meeting in New Orleans. It is an online intellectual community for emerging and established scholars working at the nexus of STS and agrifood. Currently housed on Slack, the group holds monthly interactive online writing workshops, and members regularly share calls for papers, jobs and fellowships, pedagogies, among other useful information. We invite anyone interested in our work or in joining our growing intellectual community to join us at this Meetup.

Session Organizers:

Samara Brock, Yale University

Mascha Gugganig, University of Ottawa

Chair:

Karly Burch, University of Otago

545. Expert/knowledge Politics in Food And Agriculture Amidst the Pandemic and Technological Change

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 13

Food and agriculture systems offer rich case studies for interrogating how the politics of expertise and knowledge continue to evolve in unsettled, uncertain times. Traditionally, STS scholarship has focused on the epistemic politics of expertise: for example, dominant institutions and actors have long granted scientific and technical expertise greater legitimacy and authority, compared to other forms of knowledge production. Now, the advent of emerging agrifood technologies – such as CRISPR-Cas9, farm automation, and big data – has reinforced technologically-centered knowledge making that promises greater control over nature while gesturing to more equitable, inclusive, and diverse outcomes. Similarly, the COVID-19 pandemic has exposed many struggles over expertise in food and agriculture. Public health experts, health departments, food companies, and government agencies struggled within and against partisan politics to establish credibility, often sidelining the embodied knowledge and agency of workers on farms, in supermarkets, and at meat processing plants. Who is most knowledgeable about workplace conditions, worker life, risk and exposure, and health and safety? What becomes of the ‘undone science’ and unpracticed expertise in realms of agroecological, field-based, and observational modes of producing knowledge about nourishment? This panel gathers together perspectives on the politics of expertise and knowledge from meatpacking plants in the US, from research and policy on alternative meats in Japan, from participatory plant breeding in the US, and the role of genomics and big data in transforming crop breeding at the international level.

Participants:

Packing COVID-19 knowledge: Racialized expert politics in the Meat Industry *Alastair Iles, UC Berkeley; Maywa Montenegro de Wit*

Racial and economic inequalities have long permeated the US meatpacking industry, with immigrant and minoritized workers subjected to exploitative and dangerous factory conditions. The COVID-19 pandemic exposed these inequalities very visibly. As the pandemic took hold in spring 2020, meat companies failed to provide testing, personal protective equipment, and paid sick leave. After initially denying that a problem existed, industry executives instead began invoking their authoritative logistics knowledge to justify their actions, aided by the Trump Administration. They obscured case numbers. They blamed Latinx familial living arrangements. They undercut the efforts of grossly under-resourced public health authorities by enlisting state and federal government officials to reinforce their power. Against these attempts to quarantine and de-legitimate local knowledge, meatpacking workers began to assert their embodied and experiential expertise regarding their own livelihoods. They organized walkouts, spoke on and off the record to reporters, and gathered their own evidence of outbreaks connected to the plants. In this paper, we analyze the racialized patterns of expert politics and knowledge production in the pandemic, using the meatpacking industry as a case study. Who has the power to identify COVID-19 risks, and for whom? Who has the ability to define solutions and judge pandemic trends? To say when it is ‘safe enough’ to return to factories? To decide whether industrial animal supply chains themselves produce risk? Deciding those questions is not neutral – they are embedded in life-worlds where entrenched hierarchies of knowledge and malignant power inequalities prevail. The consequences have been profound: As of early March 2021, at least 57,526 meatpacking workers have tested positive, and 284 have died.

Digital infrastructures of agrobiodiversity and the (im)materialities of seed work *Christian Brooks Keeve, University Of Kentucky*

This paper seeks to address the co-production of digital and material nonhuman lives through practices of in situ agrobiodiversity conversation, or the periodic saving and

growing out of open-pollinated crop varieties. Seeds are being increasingly turned toward for political projects around locally and regionally sustainable food systems, but also individual practices of ecological and historical meaning-making through reconnections with ancestral food. Although seedkeeping and plant breeding projects, from agricultural institutions to homegardens, consist of engagements with and shifts among local ecologies, I explore the knowledge politics behind contemporary seed cultures, notably how selection and trait ontologies are negotiated between farmers, gardeners, and plant breeders increasingly through digital platforms. I ground this in an analysis of the company Truelove Seeds and a plant breeding startup, SeedLinked, conducting discourse analyses of their web presences. I bolster this with a digital archival study of a selection of culturally significant crop varieties, comparing their discursive and visual lives with catalogs in the USDA Special Collections. I hope to demonstrate the ways in which the intimate ecologies of seed and garden cultures are produced by and mediated through digital space, and how the turn toward digital platforms for participatory plant breeding may work with and against the sustainability of local agricultural knowledge systems. This puts the human into digital-ecological encounter with the more-than-human, as well as with ancestral and cultural histories. It also raises questions about the impact of digital infrastructures on the physical landscapes of agrobiodiversity and in situ conservation projects.

The Politics of Technologically-centered Knowledge in the Making of Sustainable Agrifood Systems: The Case of Emerging Food Technologies in Japan *Tomiko Yamaguchi, International Christian University*

This paper examines the politics of technologically-centered knowledge in the making of sustainable agrifood systems. The focus is on the ways in which technoscientific expertise is positioned in policy roadmaps as a key to shifting to a sustainable society. In Japan, the problem of achieving sustainable food production and consumption seems to be particularly complex, involving pressures such as a declining food self-sufficiency ratio and an aging and declining farm population. In discussion of these issues, the technoscientific approach is framed as a legitimate way to move toward a vision of sustainability, in preference to other approaches. Against this backdrop and as a way to examine the politics surrounding technologically-centered knowledge, this paper uses the notion of ‘contract’ to examine how emerging food technologies such as cultured meat, gene-edited foods, and alternatives sources of protein such as insect-based proteins are positioned within policy roadmaps. The analysis focuses on what these technologies will do, why they should be used, and the appropriate conditions for their further development. Using the case study approach, I argue that the contract for these technologies have powerful performative effects that provide momentum for the furtherance of these innovations.

Post-Genomic Plant Breeding: Shifting Expertise and Agricultural Knowledge in a Data-Driven Regime *Hugh Francis Williamson, University of Exeter*

International agricultural research institutes and funders, including the CGIAR and the Gates Foundation, have recently begun to implement large-scale reorganisations of crop breeding networks, with the aim of making breeding a more data-driven activity and rationalising the development of new crop varieties for low- and middle-income countries. This vision of data-driven breeding is multifaceted. It includes the expansion of market research methods to develop formal product profiles that structure the goals of breeding, as well as the use of envirotyping and climate modelling to guide the selection of source germplasm for breeding in the face of climate change. Most significantly, it has been driven by the increasing availability of genomic selection technologies that utilise high-throughput

genotyping and statistical modelling to make rapid decisions about the selection of individual plants even before they have reached maturity in the field. These changes have significant implications regarding the place of expertise in crop breeding and agricultural research, and especially the displacement of diverse forms of expertise (including embodied and local knowledge) from hard-won positions in agricultural research networks. (For example, participatory plant breeding methods have been characterised as little more than a poor form of market research). This paper draws on ongoing ethnographic and collaborative research with plant scientists, breeders and other stakeholders, as well as perspectives from critical data studies, to analyse the politics of farmer knowledge, participation and co-production in a data-driven scientific regime. It focuses especially on the possibilities and limitations for democratic negotiation of environmental futures in agricultural landscapes.

Session Organizers:

Alastair Iles, UC Berkeley

Maywa Montenegro de Wit

546. Feminist STS / FiSTS (Feminists in Science and Technology Studies) Annual 4S Meetup

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 14

Feminists in Science and Technology Studies (FiSTS) Annual Meetup. All interested in Feminist STS are welcome.

Session Organizer:

Evangelina (Vange) Heiliger, Smith College American Studies

Chair:

Ashton Wesner, Colby College

547. Thinking with Katherine McKittrick's Dear Science and Other Stories

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 15

In this panel, junior, senior, and independent scholars in and around Feminist Science and Technology Studies aim to center racism, colonialism, imperialism, antiblackness, heteropatriarchy, and white supremacy in their feminist STS analysis (for examples see Chen 2012; Roberts 2012; Pollock and Subramaniam 2016; Willey 2016; Tallbear 2017, 2013; Nelson 2016; Bailey and Whitney 2017; Noble 2018; Prescod-Weinstein 2020). Inspired by Katherine McKittrick's recent book *Dear Science and Other Stories* (2021) this panel brings together papers on different valences, orientations, and relationships with McKittrick's work. From distinct areas of study across evolutionary biology, botany, postgenomics, physics, and art we take up the question that McKittrick's book opens up: how can we embrace new methodologies, analytics, and frameworks that breach "inequitable systems of knowledge" (2021:153)? We take up McKittrick's critique of feminist STS, and the ways in which the literature has reinforced a biocentric view of the world, by replicating the very ideas it has critiqued. This panel takes seriously McKittrick's call to "breach" the "autopoiesis" of scientific knowledge production that perpetuates antiblackness (2020: 2).

Participants:

Haunted Archives of Livingness *Banu Subramaniam*,

University of Massachusetts Amherst

Katherine McKittrick's *Dear Science and Other Stories* is an urgent call to rethink science's and STS's engagement with the legacies of race, racism, slavery, settler colonialism, and white supremacy. In a trenchant critique, McKittrick argues that feminist STS's critiques of biology, and biological determinism have often reinforced and re-centered a colonial imaginary. She pushes us to think behind the abject figure of the haunted archive, and reminds us that there is also wonder, creativity, beauty, and joy in black livingness and relations. Using the case of botany, this paper engages McKittrick to explore other archives, and other histories of livingness.

Postgenomic Autopoiesis *Natali Valdez, Wellesley College*

In *Dear Science*, McKittrick explains autopoiesis as a "recursive logic; [that] depicts our presently ecocidal and genocidal world as normal and unalterable" (2021:2). Autopoiesis is a way to describe the maintenance of the status quo, and the limiting belief that nothing can be changed. In this paper, I explore the relevance of autopoiesis to the production of evidence-based medicine, and postgenomic reproduction. In my ethnographic research on clinical trials in the US and UK that target overweight and ethnically diverse pregnant populations for lifestyle interventions, I found that the content of prenatal interventions have not significantly changed since the 1950s. In addition, regardless of a postgenomic era and emergent epigenetic theories on biological plasticity, the conceptual frameworks, methods, and standards employed in contemporary pregnancy trials remain fundamentally unaltered across the past 40 years. And, despite 30 years of diversity and inclusion efforts in publicly funded clinical trials, there is still a public health crisis of systemic racism. Thinking with McKittrick, I ask how can feminists STS scholars spot light areas for change, and "breach" the autopoiesis in evidence-based medicine and postgenomic reproduction?

Theorizing Eros (They Cannot Have Everything) *Angela Willey, University of Massachusetts, Amherst*

In *Dear Science and Other Stories*, Katherine McKittrick offers an arresting meditation on the violence of positivism. The will to knowledge, even in our counter-narratives and elegant histories of science's harms, objectifies, distorts, and forecloses possibilities. McKittrick's poetics disrupt the persistent drive of academic logics of knowledge accumulation. "Stop her autopsy" she writes, "they cannot have everything." So much energy is expended trying to rewrite and revise scientific storytelling about sexuality, to show that the category has a history, that it's intimate co-formation with colonialism and anti-black racism are the conditions of its intelligibility today. And social scientists do their best to "account" for those histories (Huffer 2013). What if we began with the mandate to stop sexual scientific knowledge making- to interrupt, or render irrelevant, storytelling about "human nature" that objectifies and contains vast interspecies capacities for being and belonging? This paper considers L.H. Stallings and Ella Pryzbylo black and asexual erotics as a Lordean provocations to undo sex/uality and engage expansively with what McKittrick might call "livingness."

Upending another demarcation problem: Black thought as scientific thought *Chanda Prescod-Weinstein, University of New Hampshire*

I argue that Katherine McKittrick's *Dear Science and Other Stories* is an important entry into the discourse about disciplinary boundaries. Ostensibly a Black studies book, through its title and content, McKittrick asserts Black liberation thought as knowledge production that is akin and/or adjacent to science, if not scientific itself. I will discuss what *Dear Science* has to teach us about the problem of defining "science," particularly in a world that is anti-Black and often refuses to recognize Black African indigeneity and the Black Atlantic's relationship to that indigeneity. McKittrick's text offers us another way of seeing science and making meaning of identities and movements such as #BlackandSTEM.

Dear Science Fiction: Reflections on a futuristic Black Scholartistry and Critical Arts Based Research *sam smiley, AstroDime LLC*

How many times do you get a playlist out of an academic book? Using themes of interdisciplinary disobedience, Black methodology as power, and process over product. Dr McKittrick provides a theoretical toolbox for interrupting colonial and settler colonial power through creative methodologies. For this panel I will riff off the themes presented in this book to reflect on Critical Autoethnography, Black Science Fiction,

ScholARTistry (Cahnman, 2006) and the false neutrality of using “Art” as a stand-in for white cultural expression. A closed loop is impermeable; Dr McKittrock’s book provides the incentive for breaking through the cellular membrane.

Session Organizer:

Natali Valdez, Wellesley College

Discussant:

Katherine McKittrick, Queen’s University

548. Beyond Food: Perspectives on Practice and Relation in Agricultural Production II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Social scientific scholarship on agriculture often focuses on food systems, but this panel addresses dimensions of agricultural production and practice beyond food itself. As pig bodies yield both pork and pharmaceutical materials, corn both animal feed and ethanol, and cannabis both medicine and building materials, how does the practice, governance, and commercialization of agriculture beyond food generate opportunities or challenges for emancipatory change and good relations? Well-studied food system concerns like soil and environmental degradation, violent labor practices, and the plantation logics of industrialism, might be augmented by studies that approach agriculture from non-food perspectives; submissions could address the complexities of agricultural production of medicines/pharmaceuticals, textiles, lumber, or other goods. How and in what ways do these forms of agricultural production generate specific relations with environments, social worlds, scales, industries, or practices of extraction? How can critical or ethnographic studies of agriculture shed light on linked or dependent industries such as pharma or construction? How is racial capitalism working in agriculture beyond and adjacent to food? What are the political potentials or projects surfacing in these forms of agricultural production (for example, climate and environmental justice), and with what stakes, tactics, demands, or effects?

Participants:

Approaching Energy Transformation With Livestock *Turner Adornetto*, *Ohio State University*

Rural energy transformations are steeped in the notion of technological directionality, whereby inbound devices and new industries are figured as central innovating agents. In this paper, I explore how locally-tended livestock are leveraged to shape, navigate, and contest the terms of rural solar proliferation in Tanzania’s Arusha Region. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork with Maasai herders and a brief review of the history of energy development in Northern Tanzania, I rethink energy transformation through encounters between actors, ideas, and materials. As opposed to studies of energy transition, which tend to emphasize substitutions within an energy system, a focus on encounter takes seriously the transformative capacity of local energies and local energy subjectivities. In this case, I discuss how semi-nomadic pastoralists appropriate and reconfigure inbound solar devices to strengthen elastic ancestral traditions grounded in the special relationship between herders and livestock. Work with cattle, goats, and sheep implicates a host of shifting interconnections (economic, ecological, social, cultural, and technological) that Maasai people use to chart values-based trajectories through solar power. At the margins of top-down strategies for development from the national government and foreign solar companies, pastoralist praxes are enacted to negotiate energetic utility along the contours of multispecies care to meet the needs and imaginaries of pastoralist communities. Attending to the encounter between livestock and solar, I argue, can illustrate how work with animals and other agricultural systems might provide new approaches for understanding and structuring energy in society.

The Brains of the Operation: Gendered Agricultural Labor Relations with Animal Glands, 1940-1948 *Nicole Welk-Joerger*, *Princeton University*

From meat and leather to glue and fertilizer, cattle have

contributed to various industries throughout U.S. history. By the 19th century, their bodies became important vessels for pharmaceutical production, requiring a culmination of different forms of rearing expertise and manufacturing labor. When considering the labor networks that agricultural animal bodies tied together at this time, can the inclusion of pharmaceutical operations tell a different story in agricultural animal history? This paper explores the intertwined but distinct forms of labor that existed between cattle operations, slaughterhouses, and animal gland laboratories in the 1940s. Informed by ethnographic fieldwork on farms and scientific publications found in the Library of Congress, National Museum of American History, and National Agricultural Library, I consider how both food and pharmaceutical companies used animal bodies and animal material to reconstitute gendered work during a time of social and political upheaval. Following brain matter from animated organism to suspended material on a stainless-steel tray, I illustrate the working ideals of masculine farmhands and feminine pharm hands as they reconstituted binaries upheld by agricultural organizations such as the extension agencies and 4-H clubs. Weaving feminist science studies with agricultural history, I argue that the tactile and material relationships built with bovine brains had to be constantly mediated as men and women interacted with their processing and end products differently across this mid-twentieth century moment.

The Oscillation of Pigs: How Generative Processes of Agricultural Infrastructures Feature in Xenotransplantation *Amy Louise Clare*, *MCTS, Technical University of Munich*

Pigs within the Western context tend to be associated as livestock, beings which through food production processes become rendered into fragmented meat products. But with the development of CRISPR-Cas9 technology, scientists are now envisioning an additional use for pigs – organ donors via xenotransplantation. Using this technology, scientists can now modify pig genes to remove retroviruses and introduce edits so their organs may elicit less of an immune response from recipient human bodies. Within Germany, research is conducted on xenotransplantation to explore these potentials and produce the necessary knowledge prior to moving into the next phases of this biomedical biotechnology. But how is the agricultural history and understanding of pigs generative for knowledge production practices of xenotransplantation? How does the pig, ontologically and epistemically, become situated within the process of xenotransplantation? Through multi-sited ethnographic research spanning biotechnology labs, animal facilities, and slaughterhouses, I witnessed how the processes and associated ideologies of agricultural production seep into xenotransplantation research practices. These processes range from the extraction of biomaterials from slaughterhouses to facilitate the creation of transgenic pigs, to the legitimization of research due to the ambiguity of these animals as they oscillate between livestock, chimeric beings, and experimental biomedical models. Consequently, centering upon the pig as a research subject highlights how this species is ontologically and epistemically recalibrated and affected through the agricultural infrastructures which contribute to this biomedical biotechnological research. This focus enables space to reflect upon current and emerging more-than-human relations, and consider agricultural complexities that present within biotechnology research.

Blighted Futures: How Argentina’s GM Soybean Producers Contest Neo-Extractivism *Geneva M.L Smith*, *Dartmouth College*

Over the last two decades, there has been a sweeping regional trend in Latin America toward natural resource extraction to underwrite leftist political revolutions (Svampa 2019). In Argentina this has taken the form of GM soybean production, which now takes up roughly 60% of the country’s arable land. Those governments making up the new Latin American left

generally use profits from natural resource exports as a means of rejecting the political and economic prescriptions of international financial institutions and nations in the global north, in favor of policy agendas that support sovereignty and social welfare to varying degrees. Neo-extractivism has been criticized by social theorists for its tendency to exacerbate environmental injustices, exposing those most vulnerable to yet another layer of harm (Fabricante and Gustafson 2015). Meanwhile, critics on the right cite systemic corruption and fiscal mismanagement as the fundamental flaws to the new leftist agendas. In this talk, I also offer a critique of neo-extractivism, but I do so from a different angle: I look at how soybean producers use their expertise of the industry to contest a neo-extractivist state. Attention to actors at the vanguard of the production of both knowledge and power will add to debates that seek to understand the fraught relationship between economic and environmental well-being in hopes of articulating possibilities for how one does not have to come at the expense of the other.

Explaining Rural Conservatism: Technological and Political Change in the Great Plains *Aditya Dasgupta, University of California, Merced*

Rural areas are conservative electoral strongholds in the United States and other advanced capitalist economies. But this was not the case historically. What explains the rise of rural conservatism? This paper explores the role of technological and economic change in political change. It studies a historical natural experiment: the post-war introduction of petroleum-powered groundwater pumps and center-pivot irrigation, which enabled farmers to profitably irrigate otherwise arid land in the Great Plains. Statistical analyses of a historical dataset – exploiting the timing of the new technology together with cross-sectional variation in aquifer coverage in a spatially matched sample of counties along the boundary of the Ogallala aquifer – indicate that technological change played a large role in the region’s long-term conservative electoral shift. Case studies indicate that this was plausibly due to the emergence of upwardly mobile farmers and agribusiness interests with preferences for conservative economic policies. The findings highlight how technological change can shape political development: by generating rent-seeking economic interests which exert influence on elections.

Working Land, Knowing Water: Agricultural Expertise Coordination in the New York City Watershed *Anna Lehr Mueser*

I bring together interviews with farmers in the watershed about their family history, land management practices, and adaptations to the watershed with the records of the Watershed Agricultural Council and the New York City Department of Environmental Protection. This paper, in line with STS literature, suggests that knowledge production and expertise practices on farmland offer a generative space in which to explore epistemic pluralism and coordination. In the 1980s and 1990s conflicts between farmers and watershed managers came to a dramatic crisis when proposed watershed regulations effectively banned agriculture in New York City’s West-of-Hudson watershed. What came next was a process of coordinating conflicting expertise practices across different understandings of what these lands were “for.” Farmers in the region treated the land as a space of livelihood, living, and producing. Department of Environmental Protection staff, on the other hand, understood both city-owned and all watershed lands as existing for the purpose of producing clean mountain water. Developing practices that protected New York City’s water supply from agricultural pollution and enabled farming to remain a viable livelihood in the region required the coordination of these different models and practices of expertise and modes of knowing and managing land. This paper expands conversations attending to practices such as small-scale farming which fall outside the traditional models of technical expertise, revealing the necessary coordination and choreography of

multiple modes of expertise in the ongoing management of vital water supply infrastructure.

Session Organizer:

Alex Rewegan, MIT

Chair:

Gabrielle Robbins, MIT HASTS

549. Knowing Platforms - IV

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Platforms and the Politics of Elevation *Rianka Singh, University of Toronto*

This paper proposes a new feminist media theory that positions the platform as a media object that elevates and amplifies some voices over others while it renders marginal resistance tactics illegible. I develop the term “Platform Feminism” to describe an emerging view of digital platforms as an always-already useful form of empowerment. I argue that Platform Feminism has come to structure and dominate popular imaginaries of feminist politics, and especially in the digital age. I make the counter argument that digital platforms obscure our attention to feminist strategies of care, safety and survival that people marked by race, gender, sexuality, disability and class must employ to survive. If we take seriously the imperative to survive rather than an overbearing commitment to speak up, then the platform’s role in feminism is revealed as limited in scope and potential. In this paper, I draw on specific examples of a growing reliance on platforms as media of elevation and amplification (from popular feminist movements to the US Capitol insurrection) and a turn toward quieter, digitally mediated resistance that are based on carefully laying low.

Platform Vision, or Sense-Making at the Digital Frontier: Knowledge, Interaction, and Organization in “Silicon Savannah’s” Produce Markets *Parijat Chakrabarti, Princeton University*

This project examines the dramatic encounter of technologists and traders in Kenya’s “Silicon Savannah,” a frontier site of the expanding digital economy. I document how a coalition of Kenyan and foreign technologists are working to migrate social interaction and exchange in Nairobi’s frenetic produce markets onto digital platforms. I argue that, first and foremost, technologists work to render complex market interactions “machine-readable,” i.e. visible to and compatible with platform databases. I show how this effort involves the attempt to discipline the enormous multiplicity of measures, values, mediums, and relations of exchange in the produce market. In so doing, this paper makes explicit the connection between knowledge, social interaction, and organization. I conclude by placing ongoing market transformations in historical context. Moreover, as platforms increasingly mediate social interaction and exchange, and as “smart cities” start to come online, I suggest that this line of research holds implications far beyond Nairobi’s produce markets. This project synthesizes three separate data streams. First, I document an episode of a platform working with a market development consultancy as they attempt to enter Nairobi’s wholesale produce market. What data did they think they needed to be able to “see” and make sense of the produce market? How did they try to go about collecting it? What internal recommendations did they develop on that basis? How did they plan to configure exchange in order to suit their data requirements? This kind of ethnographic data is quite rare—it is forward-looking; it prefigures change; it is an idealized view of how a platform attempts to “see” the market; and it reveals the kind of social infrastructure that facilitates the construction of a very particular type of knowledge. Platforms demand a particular kind of data; and that data only exists insofar as platforms or supporting institutions create the infrastructure for it. Second, I

develop a comparative perspective by analyzing over 400 hours of ethnographic data to show how wholesale traders “see” and make sense of the market. Finally, I conduct interviews with platform managers and data scientists to contextualize my ethnographic data and explore the limits of its external validity.

Putting platforms to the test: How data donations negotiate the value of platform data *Danny Lämmerhirt, University of Siegen, Germany*

Novel infrastructures such as data donations receive increasing attention as a way to address big tech, its business model, or issues of algorithmic profiling. But what is their relation to commercial platforms, as well as their politics? STS-informed platform studies might ask how platforms create dependencies for data donations, organising data flows and inscribing themselves through software elements (cf. Helmond 2015, Blanke and Pybus 2020) as infrastructural components (Plantin et al. 2018) for data access. This critique tends to consider platforms as core and periphery (Anable 2018) that can readily be “plugged into” (Bogost and Montfort 2009) and “built upon” (Bratton 2015). Instead, I suggest platforms as methodological entanglements (Law 2004; Lury and Wakeford 2012) and a way of co-producing people, technologies, and knowledge (Jasanoff 2004). While platforms develop the sociotechnical conditions for the valuation of platform data (Gerlitz 2016), they also depend on actors incorporating their data. In this paper, I study data donations as public tests for platforms (Marres 2013; 2020). Using wearable data donations for fever predictions, I analyse their “source code of participation” (Kelty 2016) and the various (e)valuation practices (Dussauge, Helgesson, and Lee 2015) putting wearable data to the test. Instead of being readily deployable, I observe how data donation projects faced various epistemic uncertainties when turning consumer data into “medical evidence” (cf. Tempini and Leonelli 2021). This has political implications as platform suitability may increasingly rely on such test sites, whose participatory formats and (e-)valuation principles become key sites for contestation.

Reflections on Knowledge Creation and Spaces of Resistance: Researching Surveillance Capitalism and Platformization in Brazil *Daniela Albini Pinheiro, University of Campinas - UNICAMP*

This paper brings reflections on the experience of a Science, Technology and Society academic on researching surveillance capitalism, platformization, platform labor, and sociotechnical resistances as subjects for interdisciplinary classes at a public university in Brazil. Through a qualitative and exploratory research, I discuss the process of researching themes, translating words and finding situated content for the classes. I explore the differences on how those subjects are being tackled by academics and what narratives they bring. While I found more comprehensive researches and contextual approaches on surveillance capitalism and platformization produced in a North-American context, Brazilian academics seem to be focusing on more situated research on platform labor and sociotechnical resistances, on how surveillance capitalism and platformization are being manifested in our context, their consequences for inequality and violence and how they make transparent our insertion in the world. I focus on bringing more specifically the situated ways in which platforms and computing are being studied in a Brazilian context, particularly around surveillance and labor management and control, so I can explore the spaces where craft and craftiness are meeting to build movements of justice and protection to face socioeconomic inequalities, violence and patriarchy – countersurveillance to retake history and space, art, feminist hacker movements, and places where academics, social movements and technology enthusiasts meet to discuss the developments and consequences of surveillance capitalism. With this paper I aim to contribute to the discussions on surveillance capitalism, academic production and

spaces and acts of sociotechnical resistance in Brazil.

Session Organizer:

Maira Weigel, Northeastern University

550. Struggles for Power, Legitimacy, and Control between Disciplines within Interdisciplinary Research Organizations - II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 19

As the scientific endeavour is increasingly oriented towards addressing ‘global challenges’, interdisciplinary research organisations are becoming ever more important. Within such organisations different disciplinary groups collaborate while at the same time vying for power, legitimacy, and control. Our panel examines how these dynamics affect the work within interdisciplinary research organisations. Unevenly distributed power among participating disciplines and, related to that, divergent disciplinary (epistemic) statuses can for instance be a risk for successful interdisciplinary collaboration (Reich & Reich, 2006). Organization members might for example experience hindering feelings of subordination, or of superiority. And if an organization is part of a wider interdisciplinary field, ‘disciplinary inequalities’ within this field — such as unequal funding, publishing or job opportunities for members of different disciplines — could be perpetuated or have an impact on the social dynamics at the organizational level. Questions we seek to address during the panel are: What kind of challenges do disciplinary power struggles pose for the success of interdisciplinary research organizations? Might there be any epistemic effects? And how exactly do the dynamics between members of different disciplines at the scientific field level relate to those at the organizational level? Organizational structures are said to reflect the power relations among constituting groups (e.g. Collins, 1981), is this effect present in interdisciplinary research organizations? Even in cases where policy makers are in charge of determining the organizational set-up? How do, or might, research organizations mitigate — for social or epistemic reasons — tensions between participating disciplines? In which ways can STS insights, for instance about the hierarchical structure of scientific fields (Albert & Kleinman, 2011), epistemic cultures (Knorr-Cetina, 1999) or (other) laboratory studies observations on power struggles, inform strategies to deal with disciplinary power imbalances in interdisciplinary research organizations? References Albert, M., & Kleinman, D. L. (2011). Bringing Bourdieu to Science and Technology Studies. *Minerva*, 49(3), 263–273. Collins, R. (1981). On the Microfoundations of Macrosociology. *American Journal of Sociology*, 86(5), 984–1014. Knorr-Cetina, K. (1999). Epistemic Cultures: How the Sciences Make Knowledge. Cambridge: Harvard University Press. Reich, S. M., & Reich, J. A. (2006). Cultural competence in interdisciplinary collaborations: A method for respecting diversity in research partnerships. *American journal of community psychology*, 38(1–2), 51–62.

Participants:

Epistemic Power and Ethical Position-taking in Conflict Archaeology *Fiona Greenland, University of Virginia; Michelle D Fabiani, University of New Haven*

Conflict archaeology is the interdisciplinary study of archaeological resources’ extraction and exploitation during civil unrest and armed conflict. During the Syrian war (2011-18), conflict archaeology faced unprecedented challenges and opportunities when looted antiquities became an international concern. Anthropologists, archaeologists, geoscientists, computer scientists, and satellite engineers were brought together to conduct rapid-turnaround studies and forecast site looting and materials destruction. In STS terms, it was structured as an “archipelago” rather than a unified subfield, and its participants were distributed across different centers of activity including universities, NGOs, federal scientific agencies, and the US State Department. We studied the inner workings of the archipelago, and interviewed 35 participants about knowledge production, data reliability, and team dynamics. This paper will focus on the hierarchy of epistemic power that pervaded the work, and the disciplinary power struggles that informed everyday interactions

within the two interdisciplinary organizations that became the main locations of conflict archaeology work. We found that participants navigated disciplinary power struggles through a set of practices we call performed separations: temporal control, scopical modalities, and emotional distancing. These practices allowed people to adopt an ethical position while ceding control over research processes and outcomes. We distill the core features of performed separation, and show how they helped researchers to navigate relationships at the levels of organization, scientific field, and archipelago. The case has broader implications for STS work on disaster studies, the role of expertise in predictive power, and collaborative dynamics in interdisciplinary research organizations.

Valorisation and Interdisciplinarity: Reorganisation of Disciplines' Power Relationships in CNRS *Victoria Brun, Center for the Sociology of Innovation - Mines ParisTech*

In this communication, I assess that tensions related to interdisciplinarity work at the heart of the contemporary injunction to valorise academic research results. Interdisciplinarity and valorisation develop jointly, and reinforce each other in the redefinition of disciplines' power relationships. I carried out a qualitative study of valorisation practices and policy within Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique (CNRS), the largest research centre in France, where all scientific fields are represented and collaborations between these fields are greatly encouraged since its creation in 1939 through funding arrangements. My investigation combines interviews, in-situ observations and documents from valorisation administrators and innovators of a project about a "smart flat", performed by marketing, law, computing and engineering researchers. Firstly, I show that the power relationships between disciplines drive the elaboration of organisational policy and structure about valorisation in favour of the STEM innovation model, although CNRS insists on the interdisciplinarity-by-nature of valorisation projects, to address multifaceted challenges. I focus on the formulation of funding programs as an incentive for valorisation and the transformations of administrative divisions. Secondly, I examine the ways in which researchers reproduce this symbolic disciplinary hierarchy during their valorisation projects, to exhibit precisely its modalities and the response CNRS elaborates to palliate, sometimes to make invisible, these struggles. Social sciences and humanities are often the poor relation of interdisciplinary projects (Pestre, 2004), nevertheless they benefit from their marginal position to appraise and reformulate the neglected stakes and thus gain recognition.

Struggles for power, legitimacy and control at a transdisciplinary institute *Karen Kastenhofer, Austrian Academy of Sciences, Inst. of Technology Assessment (ITA)*

The Austrian Institute of Technology Assessment (ITA) was established in the 1980s at the Austrian Academy of Sciences with a vision and mission "to understand the complex interplay between technology and society from multiple perspectives, to concomitantly analyse technology development, and to contribute to socially responsible technology policy by advising policy-makers and society" (ITA mission statement). With researchers stemming from the humanities, sciences and engineering, ITA upholds interdisciplinarity as a fundamental working principle and fosters interdisciplinarity not only with its multidisciplinary staffing policy, but also with distinct formats of and rules for multidisciplinary exchange and collaboration. During an internal research project "from within", we studied our own practices – mostly with a view to shed light on how policy advisory activities are undertaken at this academic research institute. The resulting interviews and discussions also help to shed light on power constellations in a transdisciplinary context. These are influenced by internal norms, but also by the norms of its environments – the Academy, academia more broadly and contracting parties. They are addressed in cases of personal struggles, internal conflicts or conflicts with external partners.

The empirical analysis shows that power struggles between different disciplinary cultures and their proponents present only one source of conflict. Controversies about the "best" or the "right" way to practice scientific policy advice also pertain to general ideas about the "best" or "right" interplay between science and politics as well as to divergent priority settings at the crossroad of basic research, applied research and advisory activities.

Fusing Knowledge? Epistemic And Social Tensions Between Physicists And Engineers In The Nuclear Fusion Science Megaproject ITER *Richelle Boone, Leiden University*

ITER is an international scientific collaboration between China, Europe, India, Japan, Korea, Russia and the US with the aim of building and operating a new nuclear fusion experimental facility. Contributors to the project come from many different disciplinary, professional and national backgrounds. Two significant professional groups are the closely collaborating physicists and engineers. This study examines the interdisciplinary collaboration between these groups in the context of the ITER project and shows that a power imbalance between the groups lies at the root of some well-known problems within the project. It argues that the power imbalance stems from a fundamental difference in epistemological outlook and from a different social standing within the wider fusion science research field. As early as in 1988 an ITER newsletter article addressed the differences in contributors' 'design philosophy' and backgrounds, and suggested a process of 'discussing and arguing' to resolve differences. This approach must have had a limited long-term effect, as a seminal ITER Management Report published in 2013 listed organizational problems that seem to have been due to physicists dominating important aspects of the project such as its design, working culture and appointment of top positions, while engineers' knowledge and needs seem to have been taken into account less. The paper employs a mixed methods approach and these historical developments are studied in further detail via document analyses. The contemporary situation is examined on the basis of in-depth case studies of physicists and engineers working on the topic of plasma control. These studies include interviews and network analyses, and draw on theory from STS and organization studies. In future research other fusion science research subfields will be studied to validate the results.

Session Organizer:

Richelle Boone, Leiden University

Chair:

Simcha Jong, Leiden University

551. Caring for Equitable Relations in Interdisciplinary Collaborations - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

This panel builds on feminist STS commitments to a knowledge politics of care and attends to the affective troubles that emerge in interdisciplinary collaborations, particularly those between ethnographers and technoscientists. We seek testimonies and both embodied and empirical knowledge on how ethnographers negotiate our roles in integrative research when constrained by what our technoscientific collaborators want, what funders want, what our home institutions expect, what we want to learn from the worlds we study, and the social transformations we envision within and beyond science. Questions that animate our collective inquiry include: How do ethnographers negotiate the politics of care in interdisciplinary collaborations? Specifically, how can we enact and advance testimonial justice, mutual intelligibility, and reciprocity across unequal power relations and differences in disciplinary cultures and social identities? How do ethnographers care about and for our collaborators, stakeholders, funders, careers and incomes, and commitments to justice at all stages of collaborative research, including project design, funding proposals, data collection and analysis, and knowledge dissemination?

What labor becomes visible when attending ethnographically to politics of care in interdisciplinary collaborations? What equitable relations become possible? How is work distributed in integrative research, and what roles do disciplinary status, gender, race, ethnicity and sexuality play both in its allocation and recognition? How do ethnographers navigate our status as insiders or outsiders, supporters or critics, or researchers or consultants? Where does theorizing end and social transformation begin, and who is responsible for demarcating these engagements within integrative research?

Participants:

Fostering technologies for inclusive employment: being alongside caring practices in the workplace *Mike Grijseels, Athena Institute, VU University, Amsterdam; Barbara Regeer; Teun Zuiderent-Jerak, Athena Institute, VU Amsterdam*

The potential of technologies to contribute to inclusive employment for people living with disabilities are increasingly becoming a matter of care: actors in the field emphasize the need of entwining commitments to inclusion with room for the speculative emergence of technologies, workplaces, colleagues and employees. Speculative ethics in more than human worlds (Puig de la Bellacasa 2017) could thereby almost serve as a slogan for a Dutch policy initiative on fostering inclusive employment. Through a transdisciplinary, learning evaluation, we have become part of the mix too. This raises the question how to foster caring scholarly relations in settings that largely share STS sensibilities about ‘inclusion without integration’? What do we learn from this process about adopting roles that resonate with those sensibilities, producing equal learning within improvement pilots and for STS scholars? A notion that resonates with conceptualisations of care in our fields and scholarship is that of ‘being alongside’ (Latimer 2013). Based on our involvement in three experimental pilots we unpack this notion in terms of attaching and detaching to each other’s caring practices in multiple relations in these pilots; between the person with the disability and their colleagues, the improvement team and the person with the disability, the colleagues and the project team, and the STS scholars and all others. We find that ‘being alongside’ can turn the question ‘how to care’ into a practice and thereby hope to contribute to debates on how to intervene with care.

Collaborative sociotechnical research: theories and methods *Caitlin Donahue Wylie, University of Virginia; Luis Felipe Murillo, School of Data Science, UVA*

The question of how to conduct collaborative research is at the forefront of contemporary STS and scientific scholarship. One assumption is that sociotechnical and environmental crises—such as climate change, social inequity, and mass surveillance—are best addressed through plural epistemologies. To support horizontally diverse research teams, existing theoretical and methodological frameworks must be reconceptualized to guide collaborators in aligning their knowledge practices across power differentials, thereby enacting new collaborative arrangements. Many STS theories describe or prescribe collaborative research relationships and practices, from classics such as Collins’ interactional expertise, Galison’s trading zones, and Star and Griesemer’s boundary objects, to Lave and Wenger’s communities of practice, Richter’s STIR, and Viseu’s conception of collaboration as care. Funders lend particular importance to a few social theories by adopting them to define the requirements for funded research, such as the US National Science Foundation’s use of “coproduction” to describe the collaborative epistemic work done by teams of scientists, social scientists, and Indigenous Arctic communities. As social scientists on one such team, we ask how research teams interpret social theories of collaboration to address the importance and the challenges of creating collaborative research practices and integrated knowledge. Based on document analysis of how interdisciplinary teams conceptualize their own collaborations in publications

about environmental research in the Arctic, we build on existing theories and methods to propose a new approach to collaborative epistemic work that strives to offset the traditional power imbalances between scientists and social scientists, academics and the public, and Indigenous and non-Indigenous knowledge producers.

STS Researchers as ‘Technology’: Leveraging Positionality to Analyse Interdisciplinary Dynamics *Ashley Lewis, University of Nottingham*

Science and technology studies (STS) researchers integrated in interdisciplinary research projects learn important lessons of collaboration dynamics by analysing the lived experience of the research participants. Previous approaches of STS researchers included laboratory studies (Knorr Cetina, 1995; Latour, 1987; Latour and Woolgar, 1979) and reimagining the collaborative process as a research method (Calvert, 2013). However, previous research on interdisciplinary projects repeatedly cite recurring challenges (Datta, 2018; Frickel et al., 2017; Hadfield-Hill et al., 2020; McBee and Leahey, 2017), indicating that more sharing of this lived experience is needed. My autoethnography builds on previous STS ethnographies to conceptualise my own role as an STS researcher into a co-producer of data and data collection tool, or research ‘technology’. This account demonstrates how approaching my role in the collaboration as a ‘technology’ leads to understandings of power dynamics and what is understood as ‘good science’ across disciplines. These findings, accessed by reframing the role of the STS researcher, help us understand how individuals appraise interdisciplinarity, setting realistic expectations for addressing future interdisciplinary collaborations more deliberately.

Late to the Party: Temporality and Interdisciplinary Projects, Notes From The Field *Jennifer Croissant, University Of Arizona*

As a ‘fill-in’ social scientist added late to a large, complex interdisciplinary project, the disjunctures and ‘catch-up’ work of developing relationships and getting a sense of the project as community and intellectual venture provided a unique breaching experiment. Based on almost two years of intermittent interactions (live and virtual) and tracking the communications of the group, from grant proposal formulation through the first year of the award, this paper argues that time operates in several registers. First is basic time management, as a matter of work practices, which are individual but also organizational and disciplinary in habitus. The second is time as part of the epistemic repertoire of each contributing field, as to the nature of an ontological unit in terms of reasoning and causality. Is the unit of analysis a growing season, a semester, a weekend, a meeting, the life cycle of a microorganism? What is important here is the articulation of the two registers, and the hierarchicalization of disciplines and practices in ways that challenge effective interdisciplinarity and program goals of inclusivity.

Session Organizers:

Caitlin Donahue Wylie, University of Virginia
Coleen Carrigan, California Polytechnic State University

552. Making Science in Public III

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

Participants:

Fighting COVID-19 With the Team of Five Million: NZ Government Communication During Lockdown *Alex Beattie, Victoria University Wellington; Rebecca Priestley, Victoria University of Wellington*

Aotearoa New Zealand’s response to the 2020 COVID-19 pandemic is considered one of the best in the world. The New Zealand Government swiftly closed its borders, introduced strict

public health interventions to restrict residents' movements, and benefited from high levels of public support for those measures. A major component to the response was the communication of public health measures to New Zealanders. In this paper, we undertake a reflexive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2019) of major government communications, including Prime Minister Jacinda Ardern's addresses to the nation, and her daily press briefings with the Director-General of Health, Ashley Bloomfield. We identify three key themes in the daily briefings: 1) open, honest and straightforward communication; 2) distinctive and motivational language; and 3) expressions of care. Following this, we argue that the messages presented in the daily briefings supported the New Zealand Government's COVID-19 elimination strategy through building trust with the audience and framing the 'lockdown' as an urgent, collective and meaningful cause, mobilising New Zealanders to support public health measures.

Following the Pandemic on Reddit: Hyperlinking Practices of Science Enthusiasts *Frauke Rohden, University of Oslo*

This contribution explores the hyperlinking practices in discussions of the novel coronavirus on the social media platform Reddit. The platform is organized into thematic sections with "science", "askscience" and "dataisbeautiful" ranking highly among the most subscribed to 'subreddits'. Additionally, special subreddits on the novel coronavirus have been created in 2020. The format of "Ask me anything" sessions on Reddit has been identified as a promising tool for interactive public engagement with science (Hara, Abbazio, and Perkins 2019). However, beyond value for professional use on the one hand and discussions on misinformation on the other hand, little is known about the informal public engagement with science among these communities of science enthusiasts online. Social media allow for a heterogeneous mix of actors, objects, and interactions of scientific nonscientific character to be present alongside each other (Costas, Rijcke, and Marres 2020), blurring lines between them and increasingly emphasizing informal communication patterns. At the same time, informal groups forming around interests or issues online might show distinct behaviors tied to small subcommunities rather than large topics or platforms. Using digital methods, I examined the sources and formats referred to in coronavirus-related online discussions by and for informal communities of science enthusiasts on Reddit and compared the use of hyperlinks across different subreddits. The aim of this paper is to contribute to a more nuanced understanding of diverse online communities' engagement with science and the role of online publics in the use, creation, and amplification of scientific knowledge.

Global Perspectives On Science Communication *Joseph Roche*

This paper presents an overview of a global longitudinal study of science communication professionals. The science communication professionals in the study include scientists, science teachers, science journalists, citizen scientists, and science museum staff. While recent investigations of the role of science communication have seen significant progress in understanding how science is communicated in European and Western contexts, this paper will focus on efforts to include lesser-heard voices — science communication professionals working in non-Western countries and in regions where science communication can be challenging or under-valued. A deeper appreciation of how public engagement with science happens with marginalised populations will support collaboration in the field and efforts to democratise science. The study is tasked with creating a full and accurate picture of global science communication in a time when advances in digital communication have irrevocably changed how science is communicated. The methodology of this study builds on the technologies that are changing the science communication landscape by exploiting the global ubiquity of smart devices to implement a large-scale programme of electronically-facilitated

diary studies to gather perspectives from science communication professionals around the world. The overall aim of this study is to examine how different geographical, cultural, and political contexts can affect how science communication professionals conduct their work and to ascertain if a greater understanding of those differences might facilitate progress in the field through shared learning and experience. The paper will highlight the challenges and opportunities faced by science communication professionals as they navigate a rapidly changing field.

How To Judge The Unprecedented? COVID-19 And Common Sense *Jonathan Weedon, Texas Tech University*

Science communication and rhetorics of risk have questioned the relationship between experts and publics and the place for and representation of deliberation about risk. The capacities for deliberation, the judgement (s) and common sense that we use to orient ourselves to the options presented in any deliberative situation, however, receive less attention in the literature. While science communication and STS has rehabilitated the notion of common sense by showing its sophistication and share in producing scientific knowledge, its status as a stable, definable capacity is less scrutinized. A more or less taken for granted notion of judgement and common sense-making may be defined as an ability to use experience and analogous cases in situations that call for decisions. However, the ongoing COVID-19 crisis reveals that common sense becomes highly contested in unprecedented situations. What counts as good judgment or common sense becomes not just a resource to make decisions, but a topic evaluated, revised, and transformed through the circulation of opinions and arguments. Examples from media abound as "common sense" is variously tied to being cautious, detecting the overreach of precipitous bureaucrats and dispassionate and apolitical decision-making. These circulating arguments show that the common sense on which we rely to make decisions in unprecedented situations is itself contested. I analyze news articles and opinion pieces for how common sense is framed, and chart the transitions of its meanings/uses as the first year of the pandemic unfolds in North America.

Hundreds, thousands, and counting: Death tolls as rhetorical devices during HIV/AIDS and COVID-19 *Claire McDonald, The Information School, University of Washington*

As a novel disease is identified, particularly one which is easily transmissible and potentially fatal, medical and political authorities must make decisions about how to share their specialized knowledges with the general public regarding the nature of the threat that they will potentially face; however, this process of translating expert knowledge about the nature of the novel disease and its victims is often problematized by the very authorities seeking to inform the public and mitigate the threat. In comparing the New York Times' coverage of two ongoing public health crises—the HIV/AIDS pandemic and the COVID-19 pandemic—I intend to examine the circumstances in which a disease's death toll is used as a rhetorical device to support claims about each disease as a threat to readers' individual and collective health, as well as the gradual process by which these diseases' death tolls are normalized. HIV/AIDS' initial prevalence in gay men and intravenous drug users catalyzed the development of narratives about the disease's victims and the disease itself, in academic publications as well as in the New York Times; the staggering death toll of HIV/AIDS is initially presented as an inevitable conclusion to the victims' lifestyles and gradually normalized, no longer being perceived as newsworthy despite the rapidly rising death toll. The sheer speed at which the death toll of COVID-19 rises, without easily being mapped onto a few marginalized communities, has resulted in news coverage which presents information about the disease as a threat while memorializing its victims.

Session Organizer:

Sarah R Davies, University of Vienna

Chair:

Maja Horst, Technical University of Denmark - DTU

553. The Imposter as Engine of Uncertainty - II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Participants:

Chameleonism: Social and Personal Benefits *Raphael Sassower*, University of Colorado, Colorado Springs

The conduct of hypocrites overlaps with and resembles imposters. While hypocrites have been understood in etymological terms (Greek and Hebrew) as deceiving others and themselves, imposters have been understood as challenging the social system and through their conduct teasing out its principles. In focusing on Roger Caillois and Irving Rosow's notion of chameleonism, I plan to both outline the overlapping features of chameleon-like conduct of social adaptability with "impostering" and analyzes the positive social function of chameleonism. The focus here will be on social stability and community building rather than a challenge to social formation. As a third step, I plan to discuss the conduct of imposters and chameleons whose conduct is a result of social discrimination, whereby the only way to survive, even flourish, is by pretending to be someone else, someone who can pass without harm.

Drug Smuggler as Imposter *Javier Guerrero-C*, Instituto Tecnológico Metropolitano

Drug trafficking is a significant factor in shaping airport security. El Dorado Airport, Bogotá, Colombia, is a critical transit point for the transportation of cocaine. By 2019 around 16200 international travelers passed through the airport on a typical day, 59'140.000 per year. The Colombian antinarcotic police capture approximately 400 persons per year, carrying illicit drugs, mainly cocaine overseas. The people moving the drugs in their bodies or suitcases have been called 'mules' and recently pasantes (drug carriers). While not considered part of the 'criminal organizations' can be incarcerated for up to 12 years. Far from focusing on drug smuggling's criminal aspect, I focus on the many everyday practices essential for the mobility of illicit drugs and the uncertainties that introduce the airport's hyper-secure space. The main question here is: what kind of travel is doing the drug smuggler when travels abroad with suitcases or their bodies carrying cocaine? Security in the airport implies a continued sorting of people and objects (Jones, 2009; Valkenburgh & varden Ploeg) and the standardization of surveillance practices. Drug trafficking infrastructures rely upon the subversion of seemingly mundane objects of everyday travel. Airport security has been the subject of cognate disciplines, surveillance studies, critical security studies, mobilities studies, and STS. They have stressed the political and social aspects plus the co-construction of airport security; here, I want to locate the smuggler as a disrupter of global rules, norms, and standards,' and a theorist who does not see like a state (Scott, 1998).

The Transference Of Impostership In The Reorganization Of Driver Education In Colombia *Malcom Ashmore*; *Olga Restrepo*, Universidad Nacional De Colombia

In 2017, the Colombian Ministry of Transport changed how the nation's driving schools were to operate. This reorganization was explicitly instituted to prevent various fraudulent practices, thought to be rife under the prior regime, such as the selling of licences by corrupt driving schools, or candidates' employment of a professional lesson-taking proxy. In the new system, according to the Ministry, only properly identified persons may attend schools, take lessons, and obtain licences. This is ensured by a centrally controlled system which continually monitors, in real time, who the student really is. In the school which one of us (Malcolm) recently attended, for the designated 30 hours of 'theoretical' lessons, this monitoring was achieved by having the student's and the instructor's electronic fingerprints taken at the

start and the end of every 2-hour lesson period. During the official 20 hours allotted to 'practical' (driving) lessons, other identity-ensuring methods were employed. While this new system may succeed in its anti-fraud objective, its single-minded concentration on defeating student impersonation and school corruption has certain unintended consequences, most notably, that it effectively transfers impostership from the possibly-fake student to the possibly-fake instruction. While the student may remain 'the same' at all points in her decreed 50 hours of school-attendance, what occurs during those hours - its quality, even its existence - is of no concern. Thus, the system will not, despite its own road-safety rhetoric, succeed in reducing the number of possibly dangerous untrained drivers.

Raising Awareness: "Occult" Journalism, Phantom Markets, and the Production of Humanitarian Facts *Jane L Saffitz*, Denison University

This talk chronicles the endeavors of a freelance journalist who I observed go undercover to investigate what he assumed to be a clandestine market for albino body parts in Tanzania. Since 2007, a spate of violent attacks against people with albinism in Africa has fueled rumors about the uses of their body parts by traditional healers and extractive laborers. It is reported, for example, that in the presumed absence of biomedical knowledge of recessive inheritance, miners and fishermen fetishize albino body parts, falsely believing in their power to generate wealth. Motivated by such rumors, Obert aimed to penetrate the recesses of a notorious healer's practice: posing as the owner of a diamond mine, he inquired about purchasing dawa (medicine) containing albino bones. The vignettes presented here show how rather than stabilizing facts to enable their circulation, Obert contributed to a genre of "occult journalism" wherein the circulation of "evidence" of a market cements its existence. Leaving the healer to wonder if Europeans were the ultimate fetishists, his reporting revealed the inseparability of violence from activism, witchcraft from science, and inscrutability from enlightenment. Thus, while Obert arrived determined to probe the depths of an in/visible social field, he left unsure of his role in stimulating demand for a market that may or may not exist. Drawing partial connections between journalism and anthropology, I argue for an ethics of knowledge production that aims not to elucidate a social field but rather, through a method of "not knowing", queer the demarcations between fields.

Session Organizers:

Steve Woolgar, Linköping University

David Moats, Linköping University, Tema-T (Tema Technology and Social Change)

Claes-Fredrik Helgesson, Centre for Integrated Research on Culture and Society (CIRCUS)

Chair:

Else Vogel, University of Amsterdam - AISSR

554. Technologies of Policing; Policing as Technology – II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Policing has always relied on technologies to assist in the spatial management and social control of populations. Recently, digital technologies have become increasingly central to police operations, which parallels a shift to more proactive forms of policing. Predictive policing, online surveillance, biometrics, facial recognition, machine learning, body cameras, gunshot detection, interoperable databases, and drones connect to existing police technologies as many departments attempt to shift to 'intelligence-led' or 'data-driven' approaches. With the current public crisis facing policing, there has been a growing questioning of the effects of technologies, computation, and data on practices of policing. How can STS approaches contribute to studying policing in its situated contexts, considering the uneven and often fraught implementation of technology? Given how little we know about what technologies of policing, or even policing as a technology itself can do, we invite perspectives and

approaches that study the material impacts of policing. In this panel, we seek to include a diverse set of concerns and methods in order to reveal new depths and breadth to our understanding of how technologies of policing and policing as technology function and transform each other. These might include theoretical, methodological, or empirical contributions that, for example, historicize policing technologies (Jefferson, 2020); engage ethnographically with police officers, departments, or technology developers (Brayne, 2017); experiment with policing algorithms (Lum & Isaac, 2016); and more. Further, given the disproportionate use of violence against marginalized members of our communities, we encourage approaches that consider how to center resistive and abolitionist approaches in studying policing. Nick Lally (University of Kentucky) Xerxes Minocher (University of Wisconsin–Madison)

Participants:

Ethnographies of Police Power in the Cyber Ecosystem *Andrea Miller, Florida Atlantic University*

In his 1997 ethnography of the LAPD, Steve Herbert proposed that police power is defined by its capacity to “make and mark space” (Herbert 1997). This paper examines how the relationship between police power and urban space is reimagined through the cyber ecosystem and suggests that an STS ethnographic method offers productive openings in theorizing police power. Specifically, I draw from ethnographic research in Augusta, Georgia, home of the newly constructed Georgia Cyber Center. Spurred by the relocation of US Army Cyber Command to nearby Fort Gordon, the Georgia Cyber Center is the largest US state-sponsored cybersecurity center to date and stands to dramatically reorganize the city’s historically Black downtown. As one center official repeatedly emphasized, the goal of the Georgia Cyber Center is to “create an ecosystem that is self-sustaining”—an ecosystem that exceeds the cyber center’s digital infrastructures and extends into the surrounding environment of the city. Within this cyber ecosystem, cybersecurity-driven urban redevelopment and related practices of displacement are attended by data-driven models of policing, some of which emanate from the very operations of local, state, and federal police agencies within the Georgia Cyber Center. Placing theories of police power (Neocleous 2000; Dubber 2005; Seigel 2018; Wall 2019) in conversation with STS ethnographies of practice and place (Mol 2002; Stengers 2005; Choy 2011; de la Cadena et al 2015), this paper meditates on how the security project of the cyber ecosystem invites a more capacious investigation into the environmentalizing practices of data-driven policing and police power itself.

Big Data policing in Denmark: The case of Pol-Intel *Vasilis Vlassis, IT University of Copenhagen*

Pol-Intel is a big data analysis policing software, developed by the American company Palantir, and used by the Danish National Police, for the purpose of “compiling, visualizing and analyzing data” and performing “operational and strategic analyses based on data from multiple data sources”. Advertised simultaneously and in a somewhat contradictory manner, as a “super-weapon”, as well as “simply an interface”, Pol-Intel was conceived as part of the Danish Police’s response to the 2015 Copenhagen shootings, following the international trend of the shift towards Intelligence Led Policing. This paper will present and discuss the initial findings of a research project that examines the use of Pol-Intel by the Danish Police, and the ways in which it has impacted police work in the Danish context. As Covid related restrictions have been an obstacle for the initial plan of conducting non-participant observation of the software at play, the paper will be based on a series of online interviews with Police officers and executives. The empirical focus of the paper will be on the effect of the visualizations that the software produces, their impact on Police investigations and allocation of resources, as well as issues of data privacy and user accountability.

Algorithmic Policing: An Empirical Study of the

Algorithmically Mediated Construction of Individual Risk in a UK Police Force *Daniel Marciniak, Max Planck Institute for Social Anthropology*

Predictive policing from risky places to threat scores has captured the imagination of both enthusiasts within police forces hoping to increase public safety and opponents raising, among others, concerns around algorithmic bias and total suspicion. Based on in-depth interviews with police officers in different functions in a UK police force, this paper addresses the lack of empirical research in these discussions. Oftentimes the discourse is informed by techno-determinist visions in which police officer robot-like enact an algorithm’s orders. Contrastingly, this paper examines the process in which police officers and software co-construct the risk of individuals. Drawing on STS, the paper reveals the complex power dynamics between risk scores as a reified reminder of an individual-focussed strategy and the operational conditions and alternative priorities pursued by officers. Particularly influential among these concerns are conditions of austerity shaping both the perceived need for the algorithm and its dismissal.

The influence of infrastructure on Turkish-Kurdish ethnic conflict *Ibrahim Isik, The University of Arizona*

In 2015, Kurdish guerrillas in southeast Turkey dug ditches across roads and streets to disconnect their land from the Republic of Turkey due to its perceived rejection of Kurdish identity. During the resistance, the guerillas claimed rights over the land. In the emergence and transformation of the “Ditch Resistance”, non-humans had decisive impacts. The ditches, combined with the architectural characteristics (too depth and width trenches for army vehicles and narrow maze-like streets) and infrastructural features of the Southeast cities caused the death of hundreds of Turkish soldiers and therefore brought about the shift of the governmental technologies and military strategies of Turkish state. Infrastructural features (such as communication, water, and electricity networks) played founding and transforming roles in this resistance. They became actors causing ‘new concepts and technologies’ and transforming ‘institutions’; in addition to providing communication among the guerillas, the Internet and telephone networks, thanks to their uncontrollability and speed, spread the resistance’s information and photographs, such as photos of soldiers’ corpses, which made them some of the main actors within the resistance. Thereupon, the Turkish government had to follow new strategies and gave new status to domestic institutions to shut down communication networks temporarily in order to restrain communication in the region. With regard to the water and electricity networks, Turkish forces felt compelled cut off water and electricity in areas where they could not have full control. Through examining the resistance process by conducting archival research through an analysis of NGO reports, newspapers, and local publications of the period, I am investigating the novel governmentalities and technologies that arose along with the resistance process in this paper.

Session Organizer:

Nick Lally, University of Kentucky

Chair:

Xerxes Minocher, University of Wisconsin-Madison

555. Emerging practices in Systems and Synthetic Biology: new social and epistemic configurations in the Life Sciences

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Participants:

A Cybernetic Life-Molecule: McCulloch’s ‘Biological Computer’ and the Biology at the Origin of Life *Kathleen Powers, University of California, Irvine*

In this paper, I discuss a new cybernetic object, the ‘biological

computer,' which is not a brain but a molecule — a hereditary, reproductive molecule demarcated from DNA. Warren S. McCulloch's contributions to cybernetics are traditionally understood as confined to the brain-computer analogy established with John Pfeiffer in "Of Digital Computers Called Brains" (1949); however, the archival document "Biological Computers" (1957-1958) (Warren S. McCulloch Papers, American Philosophical Society Library) requires a reconsideration of McCulloch's contribution from the perspective of the life sciences. McCulloch was a physician, and in "Biological Computers," we are presented with a cybernetic origin story: how the body begins and develops under the aegis of a set of proteins as life-molecules called 'biological computers.' Cybernetics has not been looked to as a science of life: because of the hierarchy perceived in the structure of feedback, cybernetics has been described as devoid of the conceptual tools necessary for understanding the dynamism attributed to biological life. Cybernetics has been counterposed with plasticity (Malabou 2008) and with vitalism (Hayles 1999). In this paper, I argue that McCulloch's paper, "Biological Computers," offers a cybernetic response to the life-question, and I reflect on Canguilhem's "Machine and Organism" (1957) to understand how McCulloch's model of heredity offers a way forward — a method in theorizing objects that can carry information while also being alive. This paper contributes to the field of STS through its consideration of a medical cybernetics.

Engaging With the Politics of Care and Control in Bioengineering *Emma Frow, Arizona State University*

As an STS researcher embedded in the field of synthetic biology, I have on several occasions felt buffeted by the many expectations, ambiguities and tensions accompanying my presence in the field. This is particularly so in the context of collaborative projects led and funded by science and engineering partners. Introspective conversations with STS colleagues doing similar work have helped us to articulate the chameleon-like nature of our engagements with scientists and engineers, adapting our roles (or having them changed for us) based on the circumstances (Balmer et al 2015, 2016). In this paper I reflect on my recent efforts to make matters of care more explicit in my ethnographic collaborations. Rather than treating the politics of care as an emergent issue that must be managed during the course of fieldwork, I have begun experimenting with framing my engagements with the bioengineering community explicitly around care. I discuss different ways I have introduced matters of care with bioengineers, and the shifts this framing has so far enabled. And I reflect on the possibilities that attending to care affords both methodologically and theoretically for research concerned with the governance of emerging technologies.

Governance of Synthetic Biology: A Comparative Study *Yuhan Bao, Tsinghua University*

This article compares the governance of synthetic biology based on the practices of China, US and UK. Through a thorough examination of the policies texts concerning the development and governance of synthetic biology in these countries, this study tries to distinguish different modes and major focus of these countries. It looks at how the meanings and functions of science and its relation to society are shaped in policy documents which try to define the strategies. This paper find that the security, development, and ethical concern are the major three key focus of synthetic biology, but their importance varies among three countries. The different governance modes of synthetic biology are framed under the basic understanding and imagination of synthetic biology. I would show that how the sociotechnical imagination of synthetic biology influences the understand and meaning this emerging technology, how the relationship between government, military forces, society and science will define the major focus of the policy, how the history of regulating technologies in three countries make the different pace and rhythm of taking actions.

Hacking Insulin, Hacking Ethnography *Andrew Ian Murray, Ursinus College; Dan Santos, Monash University (Australia); Nicole Fott, University of California, San Francisco*

The Open Insulin Foundation—previously the Open Insulin Project—is a community-lab based effort to produce affordable synthetic insulin. Open Insulin emerges at the intersection of synthetic biology, community and citizen science, free software and hacking, and pharmaceutical activism. This mixed lineage combines with the pressing insulin affordability crisis in the United States and elsewhere to create a project that presents new opportunities for ethnographic science and technology studies methods in interdisciplinary collaborations oriented toward and sustained by common care and concern. ELSI approaches—including those in core institutions of synthetic biology—have attempted to embed social scientists into technoscientific research, but they have often struggled to integrate the work of social and natural scientists and engineers and rhetorically and practically place "social implications" downstream from technological development. Ethnographers of social movements, on the other hand, have often pushed the boundaries of embedded research-as-intervention but have rarely included technoscientific development within their purview. By recognizing the mixed heritages of synthetic biology and social movement in Open Insulin and combining the strands of ethnographic research developed and best suited to study its constituent strands, we argue that the project presents a unique opportunity for methodological reinvention. Open Insulin provides an environment in which interdisciplinary collaborators share an understanding of the political nature of their work and that social concerns are being built into technological artifacts "upstream." As researchers working as members of Open Insulin, we explore the project's opportunities and challenges for ethnographic, collaborative, and transdisciplinary knowledge production.

Implementation and systematization of RRI assessment model on emerging science and technology *Ryuma Shineha, Osaka University*

Although the rapid progress of science and technology has brought a lot of benefits to our society, the importance to examine ethical and social issues have also been recognized. However, each emerging science field have common structural issues and their own specific contextual issues. Therefore, assessment scheme should be built to understand both of RRI agendas on each field. This paper discussed the current trials for research project on "Implementation and systematization of RRI assessment model on emerging science and technology" funded by JST-RISTEX of Japan. This project aims to build a sophisticated assessment approach on RRI agendas on emerging sciences. In this project, we are exploring and analyzing RRI agendas and establish bottom-up deliberation on them, collaborating with emerging fields such as stem cell research, genome editing, brain science, molecular robotics, and synthetic biology. Our assessment on RRI agendas is conducted, combining media analysis, questionnaire, scenario workshop, scanning, and public dialogue. And horizontal comparison of RRI agendas extracted by this scheme also has been conducted. Through this project, we gained common structural framings of RRI on emerging science, and specific framings according to each emerging fields. We will report overview of them and discuss the further issues to conduct general approaches on RRI assessment of RRI agendas.

STS, Open Science, and the New Pathogen Genomics *Stephen Mollrem, The University of Texas Medical Branch*

The paper describes some Science and Technology Studies (STS)-informed approaches for studying what I call "the new pathogen genomics." The new pathogen genomics is an interdisciplinary field of infectious disease research and public health practice that has grown enormously during the past two

decades. The field encompasses the full assemblage of processes, norms, institutions, tools, people, and entities that facilitate analyses of pathogen genetic sequence data, often within or through open data infrastructures. Genomic epidemiologists deploy methodologies as open source software tools and maintain them in online repositories, following best practices in open science. Genomic or “molecular” epidemiology is the use of phylogenetic methods to analyze mutations in pathogen genetic sequences in population datasets in order to better understand an array of disease dynamics. For example, phylogenetic software packages allow researchers to study pathogen transmission patterns, to discern if pathogens are evolving to be more transmissible, and to identify the development of antimicrobial resistance in population datasets. Genomic epidemiology has expanded in part because of the reduced cost of genetic sequencing, the greater accessibility of pathogen genomic data in open data infrastructures, and the wide availability of new phylogenetic methodologies. This talk describes the new pathogen genomics and some approaches for studying this blossoming area of infectious disease research and practice that are informed by methods from STS and critical bioethics. I draw upon ongoing fieldwork, qualitative research, and policy research about developments in M. Tuberculosis, HIV, and SARS-CoV-2 genomics to propose several “rules” for studying the new pathogen genomics.

Session Organizer:

Alessandro Blasimme, ETH Zurich

556. Feminist/Critical Race STS Approaches to STEM Education & Collaboration Meetup

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 24

An increasing number of STS scholars are teaching classes and creating curriculum whose main audience is STEM students and researchers. This meetup will be a forum to share the work we are doing. We plan to discuss potential avenues to collaborate and disseminate our work. We are particularly interested publishing leading work in this area. In past 4S conferences, panels such as Teaching Interdependent Agency: Feminist STS Approaches to STEM Pedagogy (2020), a triple panel organized by Kalindi Vora (UC Davis), Anita Say Chan (University of Illinois, Urbana-Champaign), and Maya Cruz (UC Davis), have highlighted these growing interventions. This meetup builds on such conversations and welcomes new voices into the discussion as well. We are particularly interested in projects that utilize feminist theory, critical race & ethnic studies, indigenous studies, trans & queer studies, and critical disability studies as they intersect with STS and STEM education.

Session Organizer:

Kalindi Vora, University of California Davis

Chair:

Sarah Reboloso McCullough, Feminist Research Institute, UC Davis

557. Interrogating "co-creation": the good, the bad, and the ugly - III

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 26

Initiatives to stimulate innovation through “co-creation” among diverse actors are proliferating, whether driven from the top-down through governments and policy instruments (e.g. in living labs, public procurement of innovation and pre-commercial procurement) or bottom-up by business or civil society (e.g. in social innovation). But can and does co-creation (in its multiple configurations) really contribute to democratizing innovation, legitimizing interventions, addressing grand societal challenges, and facilitating sociotechnical transitions? How is co-creation enacted in practice? How do power asymmetries and incumbency shape co-creation outcomes? What are the possibilities and problems of efforts to scale-up co-creation across different locations? And how should we interrogate the practices, rhetoric, and normative implications of co-creation? In this

panel, we interrogate the processes, practices, problems, publics and power structures surrounding the inflationary use of “co-creation” as remedy for innovation skepticism and democratic deficits — often combined with effort of up-scaling and replication its processes and results. We welcome empirical cases drawing on a variety of methods, analyses of co-creative practices that build on extant concepts in STS and neighboring fields, and new theoretical and conceptual developments. Comparative approaches across national boundaries, co-creation instruments, and technological domains and applications are more than welcome. Session 3 includes presentations that examine the role of policy and public authorities in co-creation initiatives.

Participants:

Remaking Public Participation with Government Agencies *Vera Yevsukov*, University of Maryland Eastern Shore; *Allison Griffith*, University of Maryland College Park; *Menal Shams*, University of Maryland College Park; *Jen Schneider*, Boise State University; *David Tomblin*, University of Maryland, College Park

A vast STS literature is devoted to improving deliberative public engagement (PE) as a tool of democratic empowerment. However, documentation of emergent PE practitioner relationships with technical experts involved in PE adoption, design and implementation is a blind spot in the literature. This study reports a rare opportunity to observe the evolution of such relationships through the co-design of three government sponsored participatory technology assessment (pTA) projects in the United States. We frame our analysis with Chilvers and Kearnes’s (2019) co-productionist participatory framework that aims to challenge PE practitioners to responsibly innovate democratic spaces through reflexive participatory practices. Rather than viewing PE events as the sole space for engagement, we argue that the adoption, co-design, and implementation process offers multiple spaces for emergent, adaptive participatory designs that broaden who participates in and embraces participatory practices. Based on qualitative coding of 30 semi-structured interviews, we trace the evolution of PE practitioner relationships with technical experts across the three projects. While conservation of some participatory practices occurred, there was considerable modification of pTA designs within and across projects because of responding to governmental constraints, co-learning, deliberations on issue framing, logistical challenges, and negotiations on what constitutes publics. The PE practitioners also diversified ways that non-governmental stakeholders, technical experts, and publics could participate in the co-design of PE. Overall, the meaning and purpose of deliberative PE is highly variable among PE practitioners and among governmental technical experts. We discuss the implications of these findings for remaking participation in a governmental context.

Co-creating in Participatory Territorial Networks. Governing Innovation to Address Great Challenges *Gabriela Bortz*, IESCT-UNQ (*Institute of Science and Technology Studies - Universidad Nacional de Quilmes*) / CONICET; *Ayelén Gázquez*, INTECH (CONICET-UNSAM), Chascomús (7130), Argentina

The COVID-19 pandemic led to an active deployment of mission-oriented policies in STI and new R&D strategies to deal with the health crisis. In Argentina, we observe the emergence of new ways of doing R&D and innovation: oriented by specific goals, more flexible, territorially embedded, participatory, and based on ad hoc intersectoral networks. These have shown great adaptive capacity to give unprecedentedly quick responses to the challenges raised by the pandemic by generating products available to health authorities. This shows a break in the historical trends of the STI sector in Latin America, characterized by the disconnection between academia and the productive sector, and the under-use of public R&D. What has changed within this year? What R&D and innovation strategies were

deployed to quickly reach scalable technologies to face the pandemic? And, above all, what lessons can we obtain to think about post-pandemic STI policies? This work aims to explore current transformations of R&D policies and strategies in the face of the COVID-19 scenario. Drawing on empirical research results on previous cases on R&D, innovation, and public policies in the biotechnology sector to address biodiversity loss, child malnutrition, access to biological drugs, and anticipating preliminary results of ongoing research on STI responses to the COVID-19 pandemic, we characterize 'participatory territorial networks' (PTN) as an emerging form to direct R&D and innovation that assembles an increasing diversity of actors towards current social and environmental challenges in Latin America.

When innovation meets decay: sewer maintenance, innovation policy, and the making of European robots *Carlos Cuevas-Garcia, Technical University of Munich; Federica Pepponi, MCTS - Munich Center for Technology in Society (TUM); Sebastian Michael Pfotenhauer, Technical University Munich*

STS scholarship has increasingly taken an interest in the relationship between innovation and maintenance. Scholars have particularly foregrounded (1) how the obsession with innovation crowds out attention to maintenance and other invisible work, (2) how innovations demand future maintenance, and (3) how ordinary maintenance and repair practices are innovative and creative. In this article, we introduce a fourth perspective by examining what happens when the decay and maintenance of infrastructures become the explicit target of high-tech innovation initiatives. We analyze the trajectory of an European project that led to the development of two robots for the inspection and maintenance of the sewers of Barcelona by implementing a "co-creation" process that involved technology developers and a "public end-user". The initiative -- and the robots it created -- encountered diverging understandings of both "good innovation" and "good maintenance" throughout various stages of the process. Our case study raises important normative questions that deserve greater attention by scholarship at the interface of innovation and infrastructure maintenance. These questions concern, for example, how safe and pleasant, or dirty and dangerous, should inspection and maintenance work be, who determines the need for innovation, and at what level of governance -- local, national, European -- should these decisions be made.

Co-creation, what now? *Melanie Smallman, University College London; Cian O'Donovan, University College London*

Like all the best epistemic imaginaries, co-creation eludes easy interpretation. Researchers have shown that for some, co-creation merely grants the cover of participation to business as usual. While for others, it opens up possibilities for radical collective knowledge making. But co-creation does other work too. It mobilises funding. It creates convening space for scholars, firms and civil society. And it offers productive ambiguity that may at least temporarily and under certain conditions, destabilise meaning and order. Work that in their own way, imaginaries like sustainability have been doing for years. In this paper we try to make sense of our own encounters with co-creation while working on two Horizon Europe projects investigating science, technology and innovation policy. We reflect on a set of research tasks in which we have followed -- and sometimes participated in -- promises, practices and policies of co-creation. And we ask, what now? What continues to be at stake for promoters and practitioners of co-creation and what contribution remains for critical scholarship?

Session Organizer:

Shelly Tsui, Eindhoven University of Technology

558. Grief, Gratitude & Graviditas as Relational Information

Technologies: Black, Indigenous and Queer Central Protocol & Processing Units

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 27

Centuries of settler colonial and imperialist research culture has devalued, dismissed, undermined and eradicated relational processes and protocols in the pursuit of individual reputation, field formation, and intellectual capital. Institutionalized research culture functions primarily by separating knowledge from the relationships in which it is created by claiming it under it under the name of a new (intellectual) property holder, the author, scientist or explorer who "discovered" it. Within STS research environments, it becomes evident that what Aileen Moreton-Robinson (2015) calls "the white possessive" is characterized by collective and compulsory willful, habitual, institutionalized and now digitally automated disregard and disdain for protocols, community-processes and relational information. This practiced, trained and mechanized disregard and disdain are the imperial-colonial information technologies that extract data and generate genocidal information logics. In this panel we ask: What methods, practices, protocols and processes--what information technologies--can we bring from our Black, Indigenous and trans- feminist queer research and cultural contexts to refuse the relations of white digital possession compelled and rewarded by commercial platforms, AI and VR industries and research economies? These papers and the following discussion are initiated by our Digital Afterlives: Feminist/Friendship Emergency & Emergent Methods and Actions on Data (FEEMAD) working group in which we learn from and across each other's traditions and contexts, to think together about grief, gratitude and graviditas as research technologies that prioritize the social relations of information. While each paper takes up one of these three terms, we conclude the panel with a fourth presentation in which we think together about what we have learned from each other.

Participants:

Grief as Information *Tonia Sutherland, University of Hawai'i at Mānoa*

While digitization has undeniably provided a range of new innovations for viewing and experiencing historical records—including 3-D scanning, 360-degree photography, and optical character recognition (OCR)—the digitization and datafication of the archives of Atlantic slavery has also arguably contributed to a distancing of the lived experiences of enslaved people from what might be described as slavery's historical imaginary. When slavery-era records are digitized, records appear and circulate in different contexts, further exacerbating the already significant temporal and affective gap between the violence of the past and the visual experience of the present, which at once universalizes and neutralizes grief. Taken alongside the societal and professional archival values of permanence and fixity, the social structures embedded in the archives of Atlantic slavery remain the same even as technology changes: colonial modes of knowledge organization, now built into the database, are often amplified by tools and features that offer users new modes of mining the archives—for instance, the zooming lens or the thumbnail image—which can result in modes of access that further commodify and abstract the "Black body." It is vital to remember, as we encounter and engage the archives of Atlantic slavery, that technological development and change, then and now, are not—and cannot inherently be—linked to social justice. Instead, as these digitization projects increasingly foster a drive for data and as researchers are increasingly encouraged to data- and text-mine these archives, the digital archives of Atlantic slavery have led to what Saidiya Hartman (2008) calls a "second order of violence," whereby the Black bodies already numbered in the archives are requantified, becoming a new form of raw material from which new values can be extracted. This presentation concludes with reflections on Dionne Brand's advice, when asked how to contend with the violence and pain of encounters with Black history archives, to "look for the red ribbon." The red ribbon can be seen as a refusal to be recorded as trauma, as nothing more than the conditions of one's

enslavement; it can be read as a refusal to be defined by documentary spaces where, for Black people, survival was never guaranteed—or even necessarily desired. Brand’s careful and poetic counsel—to approach the archives of Black history with an eye toward liberation—evokes refusal and resilience, while at the same time acknowledging the very real affective trauma that often results from encounters at the intersection of the lived experience of Blackness and the digital afterlives of Atlantic slavery archives.

Indigenous Collaborative Community Models: A Web of Relations *Jennifer Wemigwans, University of Toronto*

Indigenous collaborative models of community creation celebrate and are inclusive of many roles. Helper is a particular role that advances a position of receptivity and gratitude over director or interpreter. This particular role invokes good relations by helping to facilitate a vision for ICT that is ethical and like Indigenous ontology, interrelated. All life is connected in a web of relations. Our interdependence is how we engender good relations. Information technology is a web of white digital possession that produces itself through a matrix of hardware harvested from the earth’s layers to create untethered connections across communities and continents. This false propaganda of interrelatedness is a ruse generated by a platform economy designed to quash any true sense of community. Employing a web of relations to information technology not only subverts the lies but upholds Indigenous ethics of responsibility, care and accountability to how we use that technology and how we connect it to our respective communities. Indigenous collaborative models of community creation provide methods and practice that produce an expanding notion of gratitude that moves beyond mere beneficiary to receptive, attuned and generative reciprocity.

“Gravid with Citation”: Graviditas as Trans-Feminist Queer Heavy Processing against Compulsory Dispossession *T.L. Cowan, University of Toronto; Jas Rault, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto*

As our departure for this presentation, we take a peer review we received in which we were told: “This piece is gravid with citation.... given that the majority of the essay is given over to examples and citations, *if* there is an original theoretical argument being made in this piece, I want to be clearer about what it is. (Anonymous 2017; emphasis in original).” The most common meaning of “gravid” is “pregnant, heavy with young” (OED). Its etymology goes to the Latin “gravidus” to mean “burdened, heavy” (OED). As white scholars raised and educated in settler colonial contexts and institutions, our work is as much about breaking the cycle of white settler reproduction (refusing to have its babies) — losing our kin, as Christina Sharpe puts it (Sharpe 2016) — as it is about being heavy with genealogy, taking on the heaviness of the violences enacted and systematized for our protection (Taylor 2020; Shotwell 2018). We propose that being “gravid with citation” might be understood as relational method of “graviditas,” which relies on heavy processing, where there is no such thing as TMI (Too Much Information), only NEI (Not Enough Information). The same goes for citation. There is never enough citation, and citation is never enough (Cowan 2017; Ahmed 2013 & 2017). The scholarship with which we are most interested has taken up the ways that digital technoculture reinforces white supremacy and settler colonialism at the level of operating system, archival protocols, content management, machine reading, data aggregation and algorithmic design. We are not particularly concerned with making an ‘original theoretical argument’ here, and believe that much of the expectation for ‘originality’ in Western academia is a colonial trick of pretending that knowledge is the result of individual genius. If we make an original contribution here, it might just be the paths backwards we trace across several genealogies of process-heavy research methods, bringing the long derided history of lesbian processing

within calling distance of more ancient and more sacred traditions. Again, lesbian processing has done its fair share of damage and has often been used as a method of exclusion and TERF-keeping. Like any method, it can be used for good and evil. But we hope to point to what TFQ heavy processing can bring to the ongoing futures of digital research practice: not only an orientation to the ethics and good-practices of process-heavy methods, but also to the pleasure, sociality, and trust in never-ending relationship-building that is not ashamed or afraid to be both feminized, queered and sexualised.

Session Organizer:

T.L. Cowan, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Jas Rault, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

559. Human Value: Community Learning Institute for Equity (C-LIFE) a Model for Building Equity in Community and Academic Partnerships

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 28

In the U.S., a pattern in health care inequities has always existed between African Americans (AAs) and White Americans (WAs) that are substantial and greatly impact health statuses. These systemic and structural forms of racism are not new and only shocking to those who have historically turned a blind eye to the dilemma of communities of color in this country. For example, with the overlay of the coronavirus and the magnitude of the spread the inequities have increased. AA communities, structurally, are now the hub for the spread of the virus because of the lack of good policies and practices in place, needed community resources, diverse perspectives, backgrounds, and skillsets to complex scientific problems that will enhance scientific productivity. Dr. Loretta Jones continuously underscored the importance of communities partnering with methodologists, to “define questions” and ensure that all team members “understand analysis structure and approaches.” Such two-way interactions can result in inclusion, obtaining, analyzing, and interpreting data that reflect community perspectives, enhancing the use of data to inform policies that align with community priorities. (Wells, Jones & Norris, 2020) There needs to be a more developed method of research assuring that the “right people” are at the table to eradicate structural racism and inequity. This panel seeks to critically foster the methods used in Community Partnered Participatory Research (CPPR) in biomedical research initiatives to create sustainable outcomes, equitable decision-making processes, and deepen relationships and trust between academic, medical, faith-based, community, and government organizations. students, community members, and communities. References Wells KB, Jones F, Norris KC. Applying Community-Partnered Participatory Research Approaches to Develop COVID-19 Solutions. *Ethn Dis.* 2020 Jul 9;30(3):433-436. doi: 10.18865/ed.30.3.433. PMID: 32742147; PMCID: PMC7360174.

Presenters:

Tonya Roberson PhD, Governor State university

Felica Jones, Healthy African American Families II

Session Organizers:

Angela Young-Brinn, Charles R. Drew University of Medicine & Science

Shari Randolph, University of California Los Angeles (UCLA)

Chair:

Juanita Booker-Vaughns, Charles R. Drew University of Medicine and Science

560. STS from the Wounds II

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Participants:

Hunger Stories from the Science Archive *Dana Simmons, University of California Riverside*

Relative to other, more mechanized, forms of violence, hunger appears as a footnote in most accounts of modern history. Why?

Perhaps because hunger seems to belong to a time outside of modernity. Hunger resists a situated analysis. Unlike mechanical mass death, hunger appears neither modern nor spectacular. Contemporary images of hungry children copy visual conventions established already in the nineteenth century. But hunger did not disappear with modernity; hunger is integral to it. Hunger is biosocial, and as such is bound to natural histories and social histories. Scientific archives let us see how the natural and the social were cleaved in specific ways at particular points in history. Hunger appears variously as a sensation, an emotion, a genetic function, a bodily regulator, an economic status, a social norm, a psychological deficiency, a cultural expression. Almost always, it is a racialized quality. Scientists made hunger and scarcity into natural objects, fit for political regulation. The scientific history of hunger and starvation in the twentieth century complicates any account, which views hunger as an early stage in the foundation of the modern world. Hunger does not happen outside the modern market, but is a direct effect of it. We often hear about hunger as an “age-old” problem. I argue that hunger has never been more modern.

“Nature Divided, Scientists United”: Multispecies World-making in the U.S.-Mexico Borderlands *Meg Perret, Harvard University*

I analyze an emerging alliance of immigrants, indigeneous peoples, scientists, conservationists, and artists who imagine the future of human migrant groups as inextricable from the future of biodiversity in the U.S.-Mexico borderlands. Nearly 3,000 scientists in Mexico, the U.S. and elsewhere signed a 2018 article in *Bioscience* (“Nature Divided, Scientists United”), which found that Donald Trump’s proposed border wall construction would doom over 94 endangered species to extinction. As the first STS analysis of representations of borderlands biodiversity in scientific and cultural discourse following the election of Trump, I illuminate the rhetoric and metaphors shared among scientific publications, conservation photography, visual art, and art activism. By using endangered species such as the jaguar that migrate across the border as symbols of habitat fragmentation and border militarization, the makers of scientific and cultural representations challenge the construction of the U.S.-Mexico borderlands as a militarized wasteland, and generate new narratives about the tenacity, inventiveness, and mutual interdependence of borderlands inhabitants. Here, I show how representations that portray the inextricability of biological, cultural, and sexual diversity open up possibilities for new identities, relationships, and ultimately, new multispecies worlds. Using Latinx decolonial environmentalisms and queer of color theory, I argue that this emergent coalition of scientists, environmentalists, activists and artists provides a distinctive political vision for the future of the borderlands in which human, animal, and plant inhabitants flourish together beyond the historical wounds of borders and binaries.

Materiality and deceiving: Handcrafted Landmines in the Colombian War *Óscar Moreno-Martínez, Pontificia Universidad Javeriana; Liliana Duica Amaya*

This presentation provides an analysis of the construction of military artefacts by Colombian former guerrilla FARC based on materiality and deceiving. By materiality we will refer to the use of materials such as plastic and fiberglass that became widespread as strategic, safe, waterproof, easily accessible and low-cost when mix with homemade explosives. By deceiving, we will refer to artisanal and skilful assembly of those handcrafted landmines to different war scenarios. This process allows transforming spaces into creative invisible traps effective to deceive the enemy by the incertitude of the location, appearance and patterns. Materiality and deceiving create an uncertain war scenario, an invisible border based on cunning popular artefacts made from creative materials that characterized FARC’s guerrilla strategy in Colombian’s War

Massive Raids, Wounded Ontologies and the Politics of Dispossession *oriana bernasconi, Universidad Alberto Hurtado*

Massive raids (allanamientos) are forms of military occupation of territories. In Chile they have been practiced for sixty years. During Pinochet’s dictatorship, they were a form of political violence designed to produce terror and dismantle the social and political organization of individuals considered a threat to the neoliberal order. In the post-dictatorship they were justified in the name of anti-drugs operations. Recent raids in Mapuche communities in South Chile represent attempts at governing a territory in the face of the extractive needs of the forest industry and the ancestral demand for autonomy of this ethnic group. Due to the evident movement from bios to geos (Povinelli) my research aims at expanding the understanding of political violence beyond the paradigm of humanitarianism, human rights and victimhood. To this end I draws on anthropologists, feminists’ philosophers and CTS scholars. Particularly I use Derrida’s notion of “ontologies” as assemblages in which human and non-human actants acquire their full potentiality (ontological value) in their interconnection with their territories to examine massive raids as forms of dispossession that wounds socio-political and material worlds (Butler & Athanasiou 2013). Rather than depoliticized, disenfranchising victims, this approach contributes at politicizing not individuals as such but the marks that borders and divides make upon these wounded ontologies including ancestral earth beings and the capacity of resistance and of reordering the world that violence and dispossession instantiate. Based on archival work my research examines more than three hundred massive raids in Chile between 1972-2021.

Session Organizer:

Mara Dicenta, William & Mary

Chair:

Julia Morales Fontanilla, Rutgers University - New Jersey, USA

561. Un/Making a Difference 3: publics, participation, cities, communities & repair

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 4

Participants:

Sharing Food as Acts of Citizenships *Carl DiSalvo*

In this talk, I will present work exploring solidarity and mutual aid efforts to share food in the city of Atlanta, Georgia. Some of these efforts involve hundreds of volunteers with defined roles and schedules, while others involve just a few folks and are ad-hoc. None of them, however, either individually or collectively will remedy food insecurity or the conditions that bring about food insecurity. And yet, such efforts are nonetheless important because they both contribute to the civic environment at the moment and also suggest possible futures of how we might live together. These efforts, then, can be understood as practices of prefigurative politics: modest acts of public and communal care and reconfiguration. More specifically, in this talk I will share how these solidarity and mutual aid efforts differently position themselves in relation to government, civil society, and the private sector through their use and appropriation of infrastructure: in the built environment, information and media systems, and with existing social services. Such infrastructural bricolage is tactical — enabling these efforts to adapt and act quickly. But such tactics also presents challenges to familiar understandings and expectations of civics in relation to the state. Within this tension, I argue, are a set of alternative practices of technological citizenship.

Public Space Crafts as everyday resistance *Evren Uzer, The New School*

Care as a framework has been increasingly addressed to

understand ethical and just approaches to spatial disciplines. Rooted in the feminist tradition, caring, maintaining, and repairing is a hands-on, and ongoing process of re-creation of, in political scientist Joan Tronto's terms "as well as possible" relations and a critical approach to the present'. This presentation will be focusing on the everyday resistance potential of making and repairing objects for public use in search of ways to engage with and care and eventually shape for our immediate environments. Public spaces that has provided an irreplaceable resource to those who need to distance, remain physically and mentally active are disproportionately distributed in NYC. This inequity can also be observed in the repair and maintenance of the amenities within these spaces as well. Concept of public crafts will be discussed through through a set of examples from NYC such as public grills, seating units, shading structures, play and sports equipment, and units that encourage and accommodate more-than-human to open spaces, including some examples from the author's making practice.

"Free to a Good Home": Everyday Acts of Alternative Citizenship and Participation Otherwise *Juan Sanin, RMIT University; Kate McEntee, Monash University; Isabella Brandalise, RMIT University; Melisa Duque, Monash University; Hannah Korsmeyer; Allison Edwards, Monash University*

People banging pots to celebrate or protest, a bed laid in open grass, visible mending on clothes, a fridge with a note, "free to a good home". In this work we build on Autonomous Design (Escobar 2017) and the idea that every community practices the design of itself. Through a practice of documenting everyday, extra-ordinary, small acts of resistance, we recognise enactments of participation otherwise. These acts confront the scripted and dominant logics which delimit how participation is considered within larger systems and structures. They serve as an opening, temporarily embodying alternatives to dominant narratives. How people make and do in their everyday life are left out of traditional design logics and histories, built upon modernist paradigms of progress and rationality (Mignolo 2007; Akama 2020), and are often seen as naive creativity. We move away from these understandings to consider these small acts as extra-ordinary forms of disobedient participation and tactical appropriation that quietly contest the norms, functions, beliefs and behaviours that design regimes impose on citizenship and everyday life through objects and technologies. We present a series of visual trajectories (Gomez Cruz 2016), documenting these acts of resistance and disobedient participation. Visual trajectory is a method that incorporates street photography and ethnographic reflexivity to produce visual understandings of everyday phenomena. The images are not just an illustration, but a resource that enables imagination and prompts action to deviate from dominant and scripted norms. They invite us to question how these micro-acts "act back on us" (Willis 2006), designing ourselves, challenging unquestioned perceptions. Through visual trajectories of these acts, we aim to contribute to discussions about the role of everyday enactments of citizenship, DIY and low-tech in studies on technology and plural ontologies. Akama, Yoko. 20 October 2020 "Archipelagos of designing" Presentation at Architecture School of Oslo, Norway. Escobar, Arturo. 2017. *Design for the Pluriverse*. USA: Duke University Press. Gómez Cruz, Edgar. 2016. "Trajectories: digital/visual data on the move." *Visual Studies: Relational resolutions: Digital encounters in ethnographic fieldwork*. 31 (4):335-43. doi: 10.1080/1472586X.2016.1243019. Mignolo, Walter D. "DELINKING: The Rhetoric of Modernity, the Logic of Coloniality and the Grammar of de-Coloniality." *Cultural Studies* 21, no. 2-3 (March 2007): 449-514. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09502380601162647>. Willis, Anne-Marie. 2006 "Ontological Designing." *Design Philosophy Papers* 4 (2): 69-92. <https://doi.org/10.2752/144871306X13966268131514>.

"We Not Only Repair Our Devices, But Also Our Relationship With Them" *Blanca Callén Moreu, UVIC-UCC; Melisa Duque, Monash University*

Electronic waste is the type of waste that is growing the most in recent years. Apart from institutional measures on waste management and valuation, informal responses that try to resist the logic of consumption and avoid e-waste have also proliferated. One of these are the Restart Parties, free public events where volunteer repairers help participants repair their own appliances. To achieve large-scale validation from administration and institutions, often smaller scale initiatives are pushed into demonstrating their outcomes with quantitative indicators (e.g. no. of repaired appliances, Kg of avoided e-waste and Co2). However, this kind of environmental metrics can overlook broader cultural values and achievements. The Restart Project states: "We not only repair our devices, but also our relationship with them." Then, what other repairs, at different scales, from the most intimate to the most structural, are happening through these caring gestures? Considering an ecology inclusive of inter/eco-dependence between humans and non-humans, and relying on onto-ethical-political proposals of feminist critical theorists (Haraway, 2016; Puig de la Bellacasa, 2017), we offer qualitative results from research with the Restarters Barcelona community. Here, we analyse socio-material forms of repair (at subjective, psychosocial, epistemic, economic levels, etc...) that, due to the narrow approach of indicators and epistemic production, are at risk of becoming invisible. In doing so, our contribution is aimed at widening the notion of repair on Maintenance and Discard Studies, as well as strengthening the political recognition and support for this type of extra-ordinary acts of resistance for more sustainable futures.

Undoing Optimization: Remaking smart cities *Alison Powell, LSE*

One of the barriers to making space for a 'good smart city' is a narrowing imaginary of techno-systems thinking that shapes the way city systems are designed – as well as the way that citizens and activists try to make their voices heard. Throughout the past twenty years a series of different technological frameworks have underpinned the desirability of optimization and narrowed the forms of idealized civic participation. Spreading sensor systems across cities makes surveillance cheaper and easier, and also normalizes and directs civic action towards ends that fit within overall frameworks of optimization. Undoing these dynamics requires a shift in the notion of 'good relations,' accepting the fragility of technical, human and other living systems. By learning from examples of 'smart cities' where data and knowledge unfold in tension, attending to the points at which human and biological knowledge disrupts and restructures technical knowledge, different ethics may be foregrounded, from hybridized knowledges negotiated around unstable data commons, to urban systems based on principles of 'minimum viable datafication'. This paper explores how knowledge in a series of 'smart city' projects exceeds what can be optimized, from sensor systems that fail (but succeed in revealing living knowledge) to social movements like Extinction Rebellion and Black Lives matter that exceed the capacity of the optimized city. If optimization promises a narrow sort of 'good relations' directed at a single set of outcomes, its undoing promises a more contingent acknowledgement of urban relationships, intelligence and persistence.

Session Organizer:

Kat Jungnickel, Goldsmiths, University of London

Chair:

Eliana Sanchez-Aldana, Universidad de Los Andes, Colombia

562. Ecologies of Empire I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

This panel offers ecologies of empire as a frame within which to detect state efforts to territorialize and materialize sovereign power through extensive biotic and geologic systems across space and time. We attend to practices and legacies of war, colonization, and enslavement by exploring the extensive choreography of uneven human and more-than-human flourishing and ruination engendered in land, water, air, waste, and flesh, both by design, and also through practiced ignorance. We understand ecologies here as natural-cultural spaces-entangled materialities that make living and dying possible-asserting that both an anthropocenic scale and the specific frictions of empire remain integral to any ecological scene. By bringing together work in and on both centers and peripheries of empire (US, Puerto Rico, Korea, India, Iraq), we seek to find new ways to put these nodes into relation. This includes attending to displaced violences, both fast and slow, externalized and internalized, that redistribute the possibilities of living and dying across emergent ecological niches. We also ask what it means to make good relations both to and within our ecologies, as well as to each other as scholars with overlapping but distinct formations and localizations of empire. We aim to convene these varied projects under the sign of allyship, rather than through a logic of scholarly extraction (how does your work serve my project), and take the occasion of the panel to manifest forms of scholarly conviviality, through parallel practices such as the creation of a collaborative panel playlist and optional co-writing sessions.

Participants:

Ground Truth: Epistemologies of the Field *Bridget Guarasci, Franklin and Marshall College*

Ground Truth analyzes cartographic production of Iraq's marshes in the Swiss remote sensing labs of the United Nations Environmental Programme (UNEP). The science of remote sensing produced real time maps of marshlands terrestrial groundcover from NASA satellite diagnostics that enabled scientists to evaluate how much of the newly reflooded marshes would regenerate and to what extent its vegetation could sustain ecological life. Unlike imperial mapping projects, which advanced and sustained British and French empires in the Middle East, UNEP Geneva lab-based adaptations of remote sensing to the 21st century Iraq war involved no ground verification, a process called "ground truthing." These purely lab-based diagnostics created a virtual reality of the wetlands that UN scientists and Kubra's organization relied on to develop Iraq's conservation policy. I argue the process of producing the marshes as virtual space was a form of violence borne by Iraqi scientists who trained on the technology as they were pushed into increasing levels of territorial abstraction while the war demolished cultural landmarks, bridges, buildings, and markets that made the material geography of Baghdad.

The Watery Ruins of Cold War Division *Eleana Kim, University of California - Irvine*

This paper discusses the militarized borderlands of South Korea, where seven decades of division and unending war have had unintended ecological effects. The Korean Demilitarized Zone has been widely celebrated as a kind of ecological utopia, a no-man's land between the parallel failures of industrialization, namely, Communist central state planning and capitalist privatization and overdevelopment. In the space between, nonhuman creatures reportedly flourish in a space of pure nature. A closer look at the Korean DMZ's ecology, however, suggests that it does not warrant an "ironic" appreciation for war and empire's unintended by-products. Instead, it reveals how the area's biodiversity is inseparable from human productive practices. This paper examines a more complex set of relations between war, capital, and ecologies. Situated in the South Korean borderlands, in agricultural districts just south of the DMZ, where the majority of South Korean DMZ-related ecological research takes place, it analyzes small, rainwater-fed irrigation ponds that are used in the cultivation of rice. Taken together, these ponds represent a pre-modern technology that have persisted because of militarized restrictions on the building of modern infrastructures. Ultimately, I argue that the ponds are

natural-cultural palimpsests and potential commons that stand in stark contrast to prevailing narratives of the DMZ as an accidental conservation fortress.

Public Health in a World of Enemies: Burn Pits and the Violence of US War-zone Waste *Kenneth T MacLeish, Center for Medicine, Health and Society, Vanderbilt University*

Over the course of the US wars in Iraq and Afghanistan, American military installations in those countries disposed of everyday waste by burning it in open-air pits. Everything from plastic water bottles and uniforms to batteries and medical waste was disposed of this way, producing plumes of toxic smoke laden with pathogenic substances strongly associated with a range of fatal respiratory conditions, cancers, and other diseases. American media, politicians, and researchers have focused on the struggles for diagnosis, compensation, and recognition of US military personnel harmed by the pits, who appear as the tragic victims of an indifferent state. Afghan and Iraqi civilians and extranational workers exposed to the toxic footprint of US war, as well as harm to non-human ecology, are almost entirely absent from US-centric narratives on burn pits. Indeed, American advocacy and veteran health research frequently situate burn pit exposure within the "dangerous" and "polluted" environments of countries the US invaded. This paper shows how US discourses on burn pit exposure, including by researchers and health social movements, reproduces an Orientalist geography that regards Afghanistan and Iraq—along with many other sites of US military occupation worldwide—as sources of threat (war and terrorism, disease) and targets of intervention and extraction (invasion, occupation, pollution). Drawing on media coverage, official documents, and ethnographic accounts of burn pit exposure, I examine burn pits as a largely successful deployment of militarized public and environmental health. I speculate on alternative or critical relations to US empire that the contradictions of burn pits might offer.

Session Organizers:

Xan Sarah Chacko, Wellesley College
Zoe Wool, University of Toronto

Chair:

Xan Sarah Chacko, Wellesley College

Discussant:

Diana P Pardo Pedraza, The George Washington University

563. Emergence in Environmental Infrastructures - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

A Plastic Architecture: An Antarctic Case Study and Future Imaginaries *Angela A Cope, Angela Cope*

On January 6, 2020 there appeared an article in the New York Times titled "The Coolest Architecture in the World is in Antarctica." Focused on the Halley VI, the British Antarctic Research Station, it detailed the portability and adaptability of the station. The station, brightly coloured red and blue, looks remarkably similar to something that would be found in the popular 1950s cartoon "The Jetsons" as it is on stilts with skis, and the pods are roughly bubble shaped. The interior does nothing to blunt this similarity, as amidst all the scientific monitoring equipment, its interior is Mid-Century Modern in its design. The station is made of plastic. To remove the semantic associations of "plastic," it is re-branded glass-fibre reinforced polyester, or GRP – the same material that the Monsanto House of the Future was made from in 1957, to be exhibited for the following ten years at Disneyland. Design wise, the two structures are visually related. This paper will examine the emergence of plastics in architecture over the past 100 years, and ask the question why urban infrastructures haven't embraced a

portable, modular, adaptable, and climate resilient built form, and instead has focused on things like LEED certification and ‘sustainability’ metrics in engineered wood and building envelopes. The future imaginaries of what a climate resilient city might look like reach back to the fifties for their inspiration, a plastic architecture is always and forever cast as a futuristic one.

Calais Then (2016), and Then (2019) *Liam Healy, Goldsmiths, University of London*

This paper will discuss the short film Calais Then (2016), and Then (2019), a two-screen video depicting the former ‘Jungle’ camp in Calais, France. The film juxtaposes footage shot during a tandem bicycle tour of the camp in 2016, the height of the Jungle’s activity, with footage retracing the same route in 2019, after the camp was shut down. By revealing the re-wilding taking place on the site, the film is a study into which kinds of life are permitted in a Europe increasingly hostile to displaced people. Formerly home to an estimated 10,000 people, and consisting of largely self-built architectures and infrastructures with little state or NGO intervention, the camp was cleared in November 2016 and turned into an ‘eco-park’, the landscape having been modified to be a home for birds, and a tourist attraction. In this setting, ‘natural’ ecology (or perhaps more accurately ‘greenwashing’) is cultivated to erase displaced people, their histories, and practices for survival. In 2019, in the camp-become-eco-park, the roads, shops and shelters that I had encountered before had been replaced with evening primrose flowers, thick scrub, a community of horses, artificially constructed sand dunes, various small ponds, boardwalks, and a bird viewing hide. These new ‘architectures’ take on a new function as part of wider bordering practice in France to prevent people from being able to camp in the space, and the bird hide and newly built board-walks provide the regularly patrolling CRS police with vantage points for surveilling the area.

Design to embrace uncertainty: fostering spaces for emergence in environmental management *Shana Lee Hirsch, University of Washington*

Uncertainty is increasing as anthropogenic impacts to the environment become more frequent and intense. Uncertainty, however, is not new to environmental managers, who have been working within a paradigm of ecological uncertainty for a long time. Ecological restorationists, for instance often embrace the unpredictability and complexity of a river or an ecosystem, allowing complexity itself to rebuild ecosystem health. Many design methods and tools are also aimed at fostering emergence. How can environmental managers use design theory to, address complex and wicked problems by shifting from “problem-solving” to “emergence”? Using examples from ecological restoration and energy transitions, I engage with design theory to discuss how fostering spaces of emergence and intentional action can produce more energy than is consumed, providing a powerful tool for environmental managers and engineers who are dealing with “unruly complexity” and uncertainty.

Session Organizer:

Akshita Sivakumar, University of California at San Diego

564. Financializing climate and climatizing finance - I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

This session seeks contributions that use STS and related concepts and frameworks to study the range of efforts to align financial flows with the composition of the atmosphere and its effects on climate. This involves developing climate metrics, translating them to financial terms, and bringing them to bear on investment calculations. We expect the many mediations between the realms of finance and climate to be sites of contention and uncertainty, providing openings for a range of STS research traditions: the study of metrics, standards, and commensuration; the construction of calculating agents through devices and calculative practices; assetization and commodification of the natural world; risk.

Here’s a partial listing of possible questions: • What is left outside the frame when the climate problem is translated to terms of a homogeneous medium of exchange? • To what extent are financial practices part of a socio-technical regime that resists change? • What processes and actors shape the mediations between the atmosphere’s chemistry and the language of finance? And an equally partial listing of empirical objects that could fit comfortably within the session: • Renewable energy finance – techniques for mobilizing investment in renewable energy. • Climate risk measurement and disclosure – efforts to require firms to measure their exposure to climate risk and to disclose that risk. • Devaluation of fossil reserves – how fossil fuel producers devalue the volume and value of their reserves. • Climate finance technologies and devices – “Climate fintech” – analytic products and platforms and how they make a financial world that reflects climate impacts • Development, rating, verification, and valuation of carbon-free and ESG financial products.

Participants:

Ecological Justice and the Creative Economy: Shifts in the Nascent Cryptoart Market *Michelle Kasprzak, Willem de Kooning Academy*

In this paper, I chronicle how emerging applications enabled by the blockchain, in particular the Non-Fungible Token (NFT) as a way to verify ownership of digital assets, has gained traction in the cultural sector. This has resulted in a schism based on the optics of the wasteful energy expenditure generated by these technologies. Fueled by online gamers and collectors, the NFT, particularly on the Ethereum blockchain, took off as a way of developing collections of digital assets. Artists and curators soon took note, and several online curated galleries emerged to supply the growing demand. In late 2020, just as interest in NFTs as a way for artists to earn money and develop a following was peaking, two key papers emerged (Atken 2020, Lemercier 2020) calculating the devastating impact of minting NFTs: in some cases, a single edition of digital art was generating the equivalent of decades of electricity use by a typical European citizen. A growing group, organizing on platforms such as Discord, is seeking change by pursuing minting options which employ the leaner algorithms involved in generating Proof of Stake rather than Ethereum’s intentionally-inefficient Proof of Work. In this paper I analyze the key intellectual and technical contributions of this recent period wherein a creative community rapidly adapting to a new market possibility is confronted with the devastating environmental impact. I analyze the efforts underway to salvage this creative and economic opportunity for artists from current excessively wasteful practices.

From Environmental Crisis to Economic Opportunity: Climate Change and the Clean Energy Manufacturing Analysis Center’s Benchmarks *James Spencer Tompkins, The New School*

Framed as a crisis and an opportunity, Climate Change has become a concern of the US Federal Government. Founded in 2009, the Clean Energy Manufacturing Analysis Center (CEMAC) researches manufacturing supply chains of clean energy technologies to guide private investment and public policy. This transnational coalition between the US Government, academic institutions and profit-driven organizations focuses on manufacturing—an interface between scientific research and market distribution. CEMAC produced four benchmarks: Manufacturing Value Added, Global Trade, Market Size, and Manufacturing Capacity and Production. These serve as reference points for assessing manufacturing supply chains of four technologies: wind turbine components, silicon solar panels, lithium ion batteries, and LED lighting. By examining CEMAC’s benchmarks as calculative practices that institute standardized metrics for shaping regulation and prompting investment, in this paper, I show how this organization establishes relations between research, policy, and markets to portray environmental crisis as an economic opportunity. Employing methods from Science and Technology Studies (STS) to demonstrate how it became

possible to conceive environmental crisis as profitable venture, I analyze CEMAC's benchmarks as knowledge infrastructure, "robust networks of people, artifacts, and institutions that generate, share, and maintain specific knowledge about the human and natural worlds." (Edwards, 2010) Furthermore, I examine CEMAC's benchmarks by applying the term economization, understood as "processes through which activities, behaviors and spheres or fields are established as being economic." (Callon and Caliskan, 2009) These concepts illustrate how CEMAC's benchmarks establish facts on clean technology manufacturing—framing environmental crisis as an economic opportunity that omits its ecological imperative.

Green Business Sense and the Sociotechnics of Environmental Care *Matthew N. Eisler, University of Strathclyde*

Neoliberal public policy's twin contradictory imperatives of efficiency and growth conceive consumer agency, corporate profit, and environmental and economic sustainability as complementary, not mutually exclusive objectives. This idealized scenario is typically expressed in sociotechnical imaginaries that tell narratives of technological solutions to public policy problems that make business sense. Knowledge-making in this context is importantly governed by the conjuring of worlds where environmental security (and thereby the security of capital) derives through the actions of the reflexive and empowered individual consumer. Acts of environmental care are hence reduced to marketplace transactions. The ideology of "natural capitalism" that underpins these imaginaries performs important political work in obscuring complexity and uncertainty in the industrial-technological praxis of sustainability, especially in relation to life-cycle analyses of energy conversion systems. In this presentation, I draw on cases from my new monograph (*Age of Auto Electric*) in discussing how policymakers and entrepreneurs manage uncertainty in the commercial electric car industry through the uses of discourses of environmental care that construct and instrumentalize consumer agency. In this manner, this presentation synthesizes topics in the history of science and technology with STS analyses of the social construction of commerce and the envirotechnical.

Session Organizer:

Daniel Breslau, Virginia Tech

565. From Hard Case to Fringe Interest: Mathematics and the Sociology of Science Reconsidered -- I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Mathematical Knowledge and Practice

Participants:

The Division of Labor and the Labor of Division in Mathematical Collaborations *Ilana Gershon, Indiana University*

Among pure mathematicians, rates of co-authorship have dramatically shifted from 5% in the early 1970s to well over 70% by 2010. During this dramatic increase over the past fifty years, mathematicians needed to establish ethics and norms for collaborating, and evaluating the value of collaboration when hiring, promoting and distributing grants and awards. The very labor of mathematics was structured as social in new ways, and as a result, mathematicians had to change how they engaged with and evaluated the process of producing mathematics. Over time, mathematicians developed new ways and new participant roles for describing what different authors contribute to a paper, as well as patterned forms of collaboration. Based on 50 oral histories about experiences of co-authorship with academic mathematicians at various stages in their career, this paper analyzes well-established questions in the sociology of science about the division of labor, authorship, how credibility is established, and what labor is seen as valued.

Group Knowledge and Mathematical Collaboration: A

Philosophical Examination of the Classification of Finite Simple Groups *Fenner Stanley Tanswell; Joshua Habgood-Coote, Bristol University*

In this paper we apply social epistemology to mathematical proofs and their role in mathematical knowledge. The most famous modern collaborative mathematical proof effort is the Classification of Finite Simple Groups. The history and sociology of this proof have been well-documented by Alma Steingart (2012), who highlights a number of surprising and unusual features of this collaborative endeavour that set it apart from smaller-scale pieces of mathematics. These features raise a number of interesting philosophical issues, but have received very little attention. In this paper, we will consider the philosophical tensions that Steingart uncovers, and use them to argue that the best account of the epistemic status of the Classification Theorem will be essentially and ineliminably social. This forms part of the broader case that mathematical proofs and their properties are best understood socially.

The Disciplinary Specificity of Peer Review: 'Quick Opinions' in Mathematics *Christian Greiffenhagen, The Chinese University of Hong Kong*

Peer review is not a uniform practice. It has changed throughout history and also varies across disciplines. For example, there are significant differences in; rejection rates between disciplines, in the definitions of originality, and whether peer review is 'single blind' or 'double blind'. In this paper we investigate the organisation of peer review in pure mathematics. My analysis is based on semi-structured interviews with editors of mathematical journals about their experiences and views of peer review. One of the most surprising findings from my interviews has been the discovery of the practice of 'quick opinions' in mathematical peer review. Prior to asking a referee to check the correctness, an editor will ask several mathematicians for their 'quick opinion' on the importance or significance of the results and methods reported in the paper. Rather than 'soundness only' (a la PLOS ONE), quick opinions assess 'significance before soundness'. We argue: Firstly, that the practice of quick opinions points to the special character that mathematicians attach to checking correctness. Secondly, in these quick opinions, mathematicians explicitly acknowledge, and make use of, a shared status hierarchy of journals and people. Thirdly, mathematicians treat the significance of a paper as fixed, i.e., as not changed by possible revisions during peer review. Fourthly, quick opinions serve two competing, and slightly conflicting needs: between an informal, private message to editors and as public evidence for collective decisions of editorial boards. Finally, the practice of quick opinions points to the current function of journals as 'labels'.

What we don't know can't hurt us? The hidden costs of blackboxing mathematics *Milena Kremakova, Martin-Luther-University Halle-Wittenberg, Germany*

Edward Frenkel (2013) writes: "In this brave new world, in which formulas and equations play a much bigger role than ever before, our ignorance of mathematics is being abused by the powers that be, and this will continue until we start taking math seriously for what it is: a powerful weapon that can be used for good and for ill." The seemingly paradoxical absence of mathematics from the typical list of sociological subjects does not merely reflect badly on the state of sociology in general, and sociology of science in particular. More interestingly, the increasing public invisibility and misunderstanding of mathematics, simultaneous with its rising importance in all aspects of contemporary culture and everyday life is the central symptom of the social and epistemic power which mathematics has accrued in the early 21st century. What are the potential dangers of this concentration of power within mathematics? And what can be done to make sure this power is not abused at the detriment of social justice? Frenkel's proposed solution - to

rapidly and radically improve the general public's understanding of mathematics globally – might realistically only work for a spherical cow, at least in the short term. Are other solutions possible, and what role has the sociology of science to play in understanding, explaining mathematization, and keeping it in check? How can sociologists overcome the negative magnetic field surrounding the mathematical sciences? In what ways can sociology legitimately approach and fruitfully tackle mathematics as a research subject?

Interaction between Math and STS: A Case Study in China on Modeling of Scientists' "Achievement-Age" *Di Liu, College of Metropolitan Transportation, Beijing University of Technology; Zheng Li, National Academy of Innovation Strategy, CAST*

The divergence of mathematicians and physicists had begun since 1900 in terms of research objects, methodologies, and value systems. Practice or pure? That was, and perhaps is still, a vital question to most mathematicians. After the "punch" from the Goedel incompleteness theorem in 1930th, many mathematicians reflected and decided to devote themselves to social practice. Nowadays, the practice and permeation of mathematics in all human fields are obvious, from digital economy, social politics, to global governance, and cross culture history studies. But there seems to be a saturation point in such fusion processes because the pure math has been, to some extent, locked in its own house decades ago and lost trust/interest to societies. How can a river continue flowing long if its source becomes nearly empty? How can a shadow dance beautifully with its own body self-binded? Admittedly, as the rise of IoT industry, digital transformation, and so-called AI world, applied math, especially computational and precise areas, will be prosperous. What about 50 years later? Can the math practices re-nurture pure math? And how? Maybe STSers could do something. This presentation would like to show the review of the studies of scientists' "achievement - age" relation in China since 1979. By Qualitative Data Analysis of around 50 relevant papers, the up and down progress was revealed, which could be an explanation of the role change of math application in such specific area. The review also discussed what contribution a STSer could provide to math study evolution (especially pure math).

Session Organizer:

Michael J Barany, University of Edinburgh

566. Good Governance, Good Relations and (Nuclear) Waste Management I

5:00 to 6:30 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Too often technical experts and government officials have seen the management and disposition of (nuclear) waste as a problem to be solved by experts, with the solution then "sold" to the broader public through techniques of public relations that are often so transparently manipulative as to be self-undermining. Instead of seeing waste management and disposition as narrowly technical problems to be resolved through techniques of quantitative risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis, they should be reframed as "wicked problems" (Churchman 1967, Rittel and Webber 1973) with the potential to disrupt good relations across a number of sociotechnical planes: between neighbors; between indigenous and settler populations; between corporations and local communities; between scientists and the public; and between state and society. Is it possible to solve these problems without toxic social consequences? We call on colleagues to draw on STS and the knowledge of its multiple ancillary disciplines to imagine sociotechnical processes that could build good social, political, and environmental relations. This might involve critique of existing processes, reportage of innovative improvements, or advocacy of novel processes. It will surely involve multi-perspectival visioning. Our primary interest is in nuclear waste, but we will entertain proposed papers on other waste forms as well.

Participants:

Nuclear waste and Indigenous land in Australia: can this be a good relationship? *Tess Lea, University of Sydney; Kirsty Howey, University of Sydney*

Can nuclear waste be a good relation on Indigenous land? Using ethnographic material from a collaborative education project conducted with the Mirarr Gundjeihmi Aboriginal Corporation in Kakadu National Park, this paper explores the technical and scientific governance of a uranium extraction operation (Jabiru and its aborted twin, Jabiluka) to argue it is a mistake to think being in relation automates positive or beneficial entailments. In it, I combine anthropological and STS methods to show the detailed labour required to decouple political expediency from technical and scientific expertise in the management of acid ponds and waste rock. For example, water monitoring conducted by the Office of the Supervising Scientist as a condition of the Energy Resources Australia licence to mine uranium on Mirarr Gundjeihmi country, used the disputability of contamination events to disclaim any contamination events. Indigenous counter-monitoring, using 'guerrilla STS', was required to contest the science, using tactics which also informed the Mirarr's eventually successful mining closure campaign. This is not a romantic story of Indigenous resistance but a salutary account of the exhausting work of pulling governance, expertise and environmental stewardship into an Indigenous-led becoming. STS-informed anthropological accounts of such efforts must bring the visceral tolls into view, lest anodyne notions of citizen-led regenerative efforts become the new catch-all solution in our accounts of the stakes.

Parameters of Participation in the Construction of Nuclear Waste Siting in Canada *Marissa Bell, Cornell University*

Nuclear waste siting has long been characterized by techno-scientific, top-down, and technocratic approaches. The resulting failures in nuclear waste siting across national contexts have forced siting into a new era. The first step has been to recognize the socio-political nature of the problem. Next is designing policies that address this socio-political dimension by emphasizing social-scientific, consent-based, and participatory approaches. The NWMO, responsible for Canada's high-level waste siting program, has sought to design such a process, centering on public acceptance of "an informed and willing host", and focusing on "community-driven" process, "partnership" and "shared decision-making". Consequently, the siting framework has many key policy components for 'success' and is regarded in policy spheres as forward-thinking relative to historic and concurrent failed programs, such as in the UK and US. In addition to differing measures for success, there are many ways to conceptualize both consent and participatory process. Drawing from interviews and participant observation of the NWMO process in southwestern Ontario, I interrogate the participatory aspirations within the siting process and its struggles for legitimacy and consent. I examine the parameters of participation, whose expertise is valued and why, how decisions are made, and how existing inequities and asymmetries are managed. While there are clear innovations within this siting process, as it currently unfolds it appears to rely on a particular construction of participation with a tendency to control and stifle dialogue, delegitimize critical/experiential expertise, and reproduce existing inequities, shedding light on the challenges of participatory governance within a nuclear landscape.

Post-political Uncertainties: Governing Nuclear Controversies in Post-Fukushima Japan *Maxime Polleri*

This paper introduces the concept of "post-political uncertainties," which describes how specific categories of uncertainty are produced and mobilized to foreclose in-depth political deliberations around controversial issues like nuclear wastes. Drawing from a set of public controversies surrounding the role of nuclear power and the threat of radioactive contamination in post-Fukushima Japan, I examine how

expression of concern by members of the public gets depoliticized through perceived priorities that are paradoxically depicted as post-political, that is, in an urgent need for immediate action and not open to in-depth deliberation (Swyngedouw 2009). Post-political uncertainties show how nuclear controversies are managed in liberal democracy that nominally rely on public participation, but constrains them so that they are not disruptive. In this way, political leaders and technical experts encourage limited forms of public participation as ends unto themselves, rather than as means for actually affecting policy. Democracy risks becoming mere public participation as opposed to participation in actual decision making. This remains an important inquiry for the field of STS, which has argued for more public participation in decision-making. Going beyond issues such as the qualities of relevant publics, STS researchers can explore how post-political uncertainties create a semblance of political participation, which not only stand as a form of tokenistic participation, but contribute toward the marginalization of science and democracy. This kind of depoliticization raises ethical questions surrounding meaningful public participation in decisions that happen at the intersection of politics, science and technology study.

Transnational Citizen-Expert Engagement in Nuclear Compensation *Annelise Riles, Northwestern University; Hirokazu Miyazaki, Northwestern University*

Nuclear accidents impact publics around the world, both as energy consumers and as victims of accidents. Yet nuclear regulation typifies the non-democratic expertise of transnational governance. The International Atomic Energy Association (IAEA) has not yet fully engaged citizens' groups in its governance structures. Over the past decade since the Fukushima nuclear accident, we have been engaged in a multinational collaborative study of nuclear compensation schemes, resulting in a report calling for a more democratically legitimate transnational disaster management and compensation process. In this presentation, we will describe our plan to bring together cohorts of ordinary citizens from Asia-Pacific nations, each with differing histories of nuclear power, with nuclear experts from both government and industry as well as representatives from the IAEA. Our proposal borrows from extensive studies by STS scholars of participatory expertise processes in domains from environmental sustainability to medical research. We take regulatory questions as involving a mix of "expert" issues and of decisions that must be determined by citizens in local democratic settings. For example, the actual zone of contamination in nuclear accidents can be determined transnationally by scientists, while the amount of compensation to be paid to evacuees must be a matter of local democratic decision-making. What is needed, therefore, is a new form of transnational conversation between local citizens and global regulators in which each recognizes the other's sphere of decision-making. Through these forums, citizens and experts will collaboratively develop a proposal for a multilateral nuclear compensation scheme that bridges local, regional and global concerns.

Session Organizer:

Allison Macfarlane, George Washington University

Chair:

Hugh Gusterson, University of British Columbia

567. International Scientific Consortia: Knowledge Infrastructures and the Role of STS Scholars

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 1

International scientific consortia play an ever more central role in efforts to address global challenges such as how to respond to major health emergencies, the development of new, clean sources of energy, and how to preserve our environment. This has given rise to numerous questions about the structures of international scientific consortia, and about how these are

changing scientific work. Which are the different types of organisational forms that these consortia adopt? And how are these consortia situated within the broader context of the scientific endeavour? What do we know about the social, organizational, and political dynamics of international scientific consortia? What kind of stakeholders are involved? And which organisational frameworks are used to deal with specific coordination challenges tied to international scientific consortia? What are scientists' practical experiences with international scientific consortia? And how do these relate to underlying knowledge infrastructures? How could the social, organizational and political dynamics of international scientific consortia be studied best? Which methods should be employed? Last but not least: what might be ideas to improve knowledge infrastructures of international scientific consortia? And what is the role of STS scholars in a process of designing knowledge infrastructures and/or facilitating international scientific consortia?

Participants:

Institutional dynamics in Research. Processes of co-creation in Research Infrastructures. *Francesca Morselli, DANS-KNAW; DARIAH-ERIC; University of Verona*

This paper proposes to consider Research Infrastructures (ERICs) as international scientific consortia. It can be observed that Research Infrastructures (RI henceforth) are defined by their capacity to connect, bridge communities, resources (scholarly outputs), services (e.g. software) and ultimately knowledge. In a recent publication, Edmond et al. define RIs as installations, interfaces or structures that "assemble a mediating set of technologies for research and resource discovery, collaboration, sharing, and dissemination of scientific output" (Edmond et al., 2020). This definition stresses on the facilitating and mediating role (and in certain cases also on the brokering role) of RIs. RIs are also strategic instruments from a political standpoint. In the case of the ERIC's, whose existence is been made possible by the European Commission, it is evident that their emergence is based on important investments and it is supported by strategic guidance especially in their preparatory phase. Finally, RIs are also complex structures themselves. Their inner dynamics are created by an interplay between socio, technical and political scenarios of different actors inside and partly also outside academia. The proposed paper introduces a novel theoretical framework to conceptualise the dynamics of knowledge production within RIs. Such framework (currently in development in the context of the author's PhD investigation) builds on four pillars (tentative term): infrastructural, institutional, community, end user. The aim of this paper is to further develop such framework by focussing on the collaborative and co-creative practices that take place in it.

STS Contributions to Better Knowledge Infrastructures for Sustainability *Anne Beaulieu, University of Groningen; Selen Eren, University of Groningen*

This presentation is based on our participation as STS scholars in ecological and environmental consortia. Our role has been shaped by our expertise on knowledge infrastructure (KI) and our commitment to embed this expertise in the various aspects of building, sharing, implementing and maintaining KIs for sustainability. Our contribution to these consortia is both critical and interventionist. Our critique of the dominant paradigm of KI is that they are currently aligned with goals of control and extraction, through an approach that emphasizes abstraction and formalization. The main values associated with these infrastructures have been interoperability, standardization and mechanical objectivity. As the goal of survival in a precarious world becomes more pressing, knowledge infrastructures need to be rethought to emphasize connection, contextualization and plurality. This critique spurs us to contribute to better knowledge infrastructures, better in the sense that they bring issues of interdependence, responsibility and discernment to the forefront and that they garner sufficient trust and reliability to enable us to act care-fully. We will explain and illustrate how our

contributions to better infrastructures are driven by three questions: (1) how can knowledge infrastructures be developed to support pluralistic and contextualized knowledge that is actionable (2) which new interfaces for knowledge infrastructures make it possible to engage with knowledge differently (3) what is the role of KI in establishing trust, and coordinating actions and institutions. These concerns guide our involvement in the service of the overall goal to contribute to knowledge infrastructures that support transformative encounters.

Relational Patterns Of Emergence: The Case Of European International Research Organizations In The 20th Century *Nicolas Rüffin, WZB Berlin Social Science Center*

The paper addresses the question of similarities and differences in the genesis of big science organizations across several scientific fields. Previous accounts of large-scale European research collaboration, for instance by John Krige and Olof Hallonsten, suppose that these projects emerged on an ad-hoc basis and had little in common in the structural terms of their creation. The proposed paper takes a comparative stance to challenge the idea of European big science infrastructures as unique, one of a kind projects. The aim is to demonstrate that the process of organizational emergence is sociologically characterized by recurring relational patterns. To this end, the genesis of nine organizations in seven fields was investigated, ranging from CERN to the European Social Survey. The selection of cases covers both centralized and multiple-sited organizations that use a variety of scientific instrumentations and have either single or multiple purposes. By drawing on network theory and systems theory, in particular the ideas of autocatalysis and autopoiesis, three dimensions were examined in a QCA-design: the continuity of individual actors in the formation process, the degree of scientific homogeneity among the actors in terms of (inter-)disciplinarity, and the network structure of organizations involved in the founding. As a result, recurring patterns in the relationality of the three dimensions are described, which help to identify similarities and differences in the formation of big research infrastructures. The results provide clues for the STS-related study of emerging and future international, large-scale research projects that are meant to tackle pressing global challenges.

Multiple roles, identities and perceptions of 'Ethics and Society' in the Human Brain Project *Christine Aicardi, King's College London; Tara Mahfoud, University of Essex; Arleen Salles, Uppsala University; Inga Ulnicane, De Montfort University*

The Human Brain Project (HBP) is a significant case for reflecting on the roles of social scientists, humanities researchers and ethicists in a large-scale interdisciplinary project. The HBP included an entire team of 'Ethics and Society' researchers from the start of the project and allocated it 3-5% of the total budget. Embedding a larger team of social scientists and ethicists across the 10-year timeframe of the project can be seen as a way to promote more ethically and socially aware science and technology, and to overcome the typically fragmented and short-term collaborations developed by social scientists and humanities researchers within science and engineering projects. Based on over 7 years of collective engagement with the HBP, this paper analyses the various roles of 'Ethics and Society' in the HBP, along with the multiple identities assumed and defended by its fluctuating membership. In past and ongoing collaborations, are social scientists, philosophers, and ethicists equals, critical friends, participating observers, ethical advisers or service providers? Which should they be? Are they considered silent partners or scientists in their own right? In a uniquely large and diverse 'Ethics and Society' team, how do individuals and subgroups perceive and negotiate their respective and joint contributions to the wider project? And how are they perceived

by natural scientists and engineers? We discuss examples of knowledge co-creation as well as the implications of asymmetries in power, status, personnel and funding between natural and social scientists in large-scale, international research consortia.

The Politics of International Scientific Consortia (ISCs): Coalition-Building and Frictions in the Human Brain Project *Anna-Lena Rueland, Leiden University*

Within neuroscience, collaborations have historically been smaller and less frequent than in other disciplines. Yet within four years two big international neuroscience consortia originated in Europe: in 2013 the Human Brain Project (HBP) was launched as the winner of the EU FET Competition and in 2017 the International Brain Laboratory (IBL) was founded by a group of neuroscientists based in Europe. How can we explain the emergence of the IBL when the HBP already bundled a great number of institutes and researchers in its quest for a brain in silico? Making use of field theory, it is argued that the emergence of the IBL was the result of a targeted challenge against the organization of big neuroscience within the field of the HBP. This challenge was initiated by a coalition of neuroscientists that coalesced around two main contentious topics within the HBP: its top-down and non-transparent governance as well as its scientific direction. The challenger coalition was opposed by a group of incumbents, mainly consisting of HBP executive committee members, that wanted to maintain the field's status quo. Using specific frames, both groups vied for political support and appealed to the DG CONNECT as well as the broader public. By analyzing policy documents, media reports and conducting interviews with scientists as well as EU policy-makers, the proposed paper will identify these frames and show that due to lacking political support the challenger coalition ended up outside the HBP. In doing so, it will contribute to the understanding of political processes within ISCs, a topic of high relevance in STS that is currently still under-researched.

Session Organizer:

Richelle Boone, Leiden University

Chair:

Simcha Jong, Leiden University

568. Theorizing and Speculating with Technology

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 12

This panel puts into conversation papers that investigate the theoretical stakes of digital, systems, and computational technologies. How do note taking technologies manifest as a pleasure-based external brain, how has the performative potential of AI inspire science fictional theorization that bounce back to technologists, how does computing allow a rethinking of the work of philosopher C.S. Peirce, how do systems reproduce? In these papers, theoretical speculation is not just applied to technologies, it is in productively generated by these papers in relation with theoretical legacies.

Participants:

The Peircean Pharmakon Neal Thomas, Wilfrid Laurier University

Stiegler approaches Heidegger's question of being in terms of the possibility of questioning itself, writing that questioning should be "questioned by the heteros that would constitute the hidden face of its autos as its pharmakon..." In this paper I argue that if the pharmacological question is transformed by computing, then one must return to the work of C.S. Peirce to best understand its material-semiotic heteros, autos, and capacity to infinitize. Peirce's methods of analysis and synthesis, his work on existential graphs, and his overall approach to signs forms something of a bedrock for the relational technicity of connected devices. Through formal strategies developed from out of his "synechistic" account of signs and reasoning, knowledge and social graphs underwrite the capacity of networked computers to reason automatically about people, things, documents, and

events. Taken up as a rich account of question and answer that models the exteriorization of thought into relational representation, and the interiorization of self into community, Peirce's approach to sense is deeply generic. But his ideas have also not gone without scrutiny, for assuming to enroll seemingly all of humanity into the endless production of "settled" signs. As a ground for subjectivation, Peirce's consensus approach favors continuity, and so he has less to say about the transformative unsettling of knowledge, which may existentially disturb and disrupt through irreconcilable dissensus. Relying on thinkers who critique, extend, and/or transform Peircean metaphysics, the paper considers what a post-Peircean approach to data might entail.

The Pleasures of the "External Brain" *Kyle Booten*

"Personal knowledge management" may sound mundane, yet this seemingly unsexy technological concept possesses is the liturgical focus of a cult—the self-described "RoamCult," a group of power users of Roam Research, one of the latest pieces of software to take up the mission of the Vannevar Bush's Memex. The core features of Roam—a popular and much-hyped "note-taking tool for networked thought"—would not seem revolutionary to Bush: users can make bi-directional links between snippets of text or other media. A graph visualization allows the user to see their knowledge as a spider web of intersecting thoughts and images. Why, in an age of much more complex technology, does a personal note-taking app still inspire passion? I propose a psychoanalytic exploration of the pleasure of building and possessing an "external brain." As Benjamin Fong articulates, "there is more to why we think technology makes life better than technology making life better" since "technology gratifies a psychic need before it does material ones." My primary archive will consist of Roam itself as well as public comments made by its creator and users. Additionally I will note how Roam echoes pre-digital visions of the external mind, including the "place-logic" of Ramus. Via Fong, I will consider the specific forms of "mastery" promised by the externalization and visualization of one's brain. Via Robert Robert Pfaller, I will consider whether the charm of the external brain rests in the way it keeps one's thoughts not handily nearby but rather at a safe distance.

Social Systems are Driven by and Continuously Reconstructed in terms of Expectations *Loet Leydesdorff, University of Amsterdam, ASCoR*

In *Social Systems*, Luhmann (1995: 446f. [1984:605]) argued that "(s)elf-referential autopoietic reproduction would not be possible without an anticipatory recursivity." Luhmann (2012:238) added that "we need a sufficiently subtle theory of time that determines the present as the boundary between past and future." I shall argue that the theory and computation of anticipatory systems can provide us with an operationalization; this can be shown by using simulations. Rosen (1985) defined anticipatory systems as systems that entertain models of themselves. The model enables the modeling system to represent future states in the present. Dubois (1998, 2003) provided algorithms for anticipatory systems, and specified the distinction between weak and strong anticipation. Weakly anticipatory systems can incursively use their past and present state for the construction of next states. A technology, for example, builds on its history, but is selected in the present. Different from recursion on a previous state, incursions operate with reference to the current state; hyper-incursion inverts the arrow of time so that anticipated states can drive the operation. Incursive, recursive, and hyper-incursive equations have other solutions. Strongly anticipatory systems are unique in constructing their next states hyper-incursively in terms of expectations. Only systems of expectations can operate in this mode, since all other systems are constrained by their past and present states into account. However, systems of rationalized expectations—discursively informed communications—are not alive and therefore less

constrained.

The Body, Data, and the Matter of Interest *Elizabeth P Bullock, Alfred State College, SUNY*

Per the theme of the conference, and its investigation of "good relations" that span disciplinary and subject boundaries, this paper considers this reconfiguration of the body as part of a technical apparatus long trained to bodily capacities. I wish to trace the development of scientific philanthropy at the Rockefeller Foundation as one place where we may begin to see the emergence of the body, as data, in the 20th century. Randy's Martin's (2015) work on the rationalization of philanthropy is considered alongside the cybernetics apparatus pursued by Bernard Geoghegan (2012) in his work on "technologies of liberalism." I propose that these overlapping developments point to the body's becoming something other than a closed system, even as the "interests" of a liberal subjectivity highlight that the logics trained on the body became increasingly probabilistic during this time. How should we connect these developments to current politics and economy, and to discourses today that emphasize an open relationship to uncertainty as part of the very formation of the body? I take up these contradictions and hope to illustrate how they are part of the fabric of contemporary discourse on social problems and solutions.

Session Organizer:

Loet Leydesdorff, University of Amsterdam, ASCoR

569. Beyond Food: Perspectives on Practice and Relation in Agricultural Production III

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 16

Social scientific scholarship on agriculture often focuses on food systems, but this panel addresses dimensions of agricultural production and practice beyond food itself. As pig bodies yield both pork and pharmaceutical materials, corn both animal feed and ethanol, and cannabis both medicine and building materials, how does the practice, governance, and commercialization of agriculture beyond food generate opportunities or challenges for emancipatory change and good relations? Well-studied food system concerns like soil and environmental degradation, violent labor practices, and the plantation logics of industrialism, might be augmented by studies that approach agriculture from non-food perspectives; submissions could address the complexities of agricultural production of medicines/pharmaceuticals, textiles, lumber, or other goods. How and in what ways do these forms of agricultural production generate specific relations with environments, social worlds, scales, industries, or practices of extraction? How can critical or ethnographic studies of agriculture shed light on linked or dependent industries such as pharma or construction? How is racial capitalism working in agriculture beyond and adjacent to food? What are the political potentials or projects surfacing in these forms of agricultural production (for example, climate and environmental justice), and with what stakes, tactics, demands, or effects?

Session Organizer:

Olivia Doggett, Faculty of Information, University of Toronto

570. Knowing Platforms - V

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 17

Participants:

Sexual Contracts of App-based Food Delivery: An examination through feeding and being fed in Mumbai *Simiran Lalvani, University of Oxford, UK*

The concept of the sexual contract visibilised the coexistence of guarantees of liberties and women's subordination across economic orders. Informed by this conceptual lens, I examine the socio-cultural worlds platforms emerge for and the web of relations they have spun. Food delivery platforms open up male-dominated work of food delivery to enterprising hopefuls irrespective of caste, gender, religion. They bring potentially purity threatening, anonymously cooked and delivered food to

the domestic sphere - a 'sacred' source of food. I examine the tension between norms and choices for workers and customers through 3 interrelated aspects. These reveal the ongoing tussle between the norms and promises of the worlds platforms emerge from and the worlds they emerge for. First, the viability of participation in this work is informed by the division of labour in the worker-household and home-cooked food in particular. Second, I imagine customers as employer-households as I place ordering in a history of eating out – public dining and the hire of servant services regulated through master-servant relationships. Given such placement, I finally note that algorithmic assignment of workers replaces employer-households' hiring calculations and minute control of workers. This sometimes leads to contestations over algorithmic assignment evident in reports of customers who reject orders from Muslim delivery workers. The findings are based on my qualitative, ethnographic fieldwork in Mumbai with platform workers, delivery workers at restaurants and fast food chains and secondary examination of newspaper reports.

Technically Wrong, Practically Right: Ways of Knowing Platform Algorithms *Kelley Cotter*

Knowing platforms requires knowing the algorithms at their core. Thus far, discussions of algorithmic knowledge have mainly focused on technical knowledge. This emphasis often glosses over the important insight “lay” users have to offer, based on situated encounters with algorithms as part of broader sociotechnical assemblages. In this paper, I apply feminist STS scholarship to case studies of user communities to document the importance of what I term “practical knowledge” and what it means for those of us interested in knowing platforms. While technical knowledge captures knowledge about the design and functionality of platform algorithms, practical knowledge entails making sense of the ways algorithms matter to and for the social worlds to which we belong. Practical knowledge emphasizes meaning-making not in cognition, per se, but via social practices and in developing a “practical sense for what is to be done in a given situation” (Bourdieu, 1998, p. 25). Practical knowledge is about understanding how platform algorithms fit into our worlds, as well as mobilizing knowledge to preserve those worlds and ensure continued membership in them. In conceptualizing practical knowledge, I suggest users' insights provide a resource for alerting us to (potential) system-wide patterns and for triangulating a broader understanding of platforms. Thus, we need methodological approaches that take seriously user understandings, and allow us to register what users know and not be distracted by what they get “wrong” technically. Without such approaches, we risk reinforcing the power asymmetry between platforms and users, which allows platforms to claim near-exclusive epistemic authority.

Uses and users design for online government platforms. The case of: Movilidad en línea in Medellín. *Sara Guzman, Université de Grenoble*

It is common in the implementation of technological solutions, especially for digital adoption processes, such as E-Government, that these solutions are not adopted by citizens, or are so at a low frequency. (Brandtzæg, P. B. 2010; Heting 2003; Oudshoorn, N., & Pinch, T. 2003; Wyatt, S. 2003). Authors such as Komminos et al. (2015), conclude that most of applications, such as those implemented in online government platforms, focus on narrowly defined urban problems. Based on these findings, it was considered relevant to investigate the use patterns of citizens, and from them, to elucidate the reasons for non-use, to generate processes for the design and implementation of technological solutions that have better acceptance. Through the application of an analysis of sociotechnical adaptations (Latour, 1991; Akrich, 1987; Callon, 1991) and of the sociology of uses (Jouet, 2000; Akrich, 1998), the patterns and processes of use will be identified as well as the translation in the design of the Platform Movilidad en Línea of Medellín-Colombia. These descriptions will serve to

understand the difficulties that users have in the process of transition of use schemes (Akrich 2010, Rabardel, 1995) from the physical environment to the digital environment, by describing the trajectories of use and digital adaptations that have (and do not have) place in these processes. In such a way, that the non-use of the platform by citizens can be understood.

Session Organizer:

Maira Weigel, Northeastern University

571. Caring for Equitable Relations in Interdisciplinary Collaborations - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 2

This panel builds on feminist STS commitments to a knowledge politics of care and attends to the affective troubles that emerge in interdisciplinary collaborations, particularly those between ethnographers and technoscientists. We seek testimonies and both embodied and empirical knowledge on how ethnographers negotiate our roles in integrative research when constrained by what our technoscientific collaborators want, what funders want, what our home institutions expect, what we want to learn from the worlds we study, and the social transformations we envision within and beyond science. Questions that animate our collective inquiry include: How do ethnographers negotiate the politics of care in interdisciplinary collaborations? Specifically, how can we enact and advance testimonial justice, mutual intelligibility, and reciprocity across unequal power relations and differences in disciplinary cultures and social identities? How do ethnographers care about and for our collaborators, stakeholders, funders, careers and incomes, and commitments to justice at all stages of collaborative research, including project design, funding proposals, data collection and analysis, and knowledge dissemination? What labor becomes visible when attending ethnographically to politics of care in interdisciplinary collaborations? What equitable relations become possible? How is work distributed in integrative research, and what roles do disciplinary status, gender, race, ethnicity and sexuality play both in its allocation and recognition? How do ethnographers navigate our status as insiders or outsiders, supporters or critics, or researchers or consultants? Where does theorizing end and social transformation begin, and who is responsible for demarcating these engagements within integrative research?

Participants:

Assembling carescape: family caregiver's articulation work in hospice home care *Anne-chie Wang*

In highly medicalized end-of-life care, how do family caregivers work with the hospice home care team to care for dying patients at home? This paper adopts the concept of “articulation work” to explore family caregivers' effort in hospice home care, involving caring practice for the dying, assemblages of end-of-life care, and affective labor about bereavement. Data include in-depth interviews of 21 family caregivers and ten hospice home care members and participant observation in a medical center for twelve months. This paper found that family caregivers meticulously articulate heterogeneous elements into carescape, including acquisitions of caring end-of-life skills, coordination about the incompatible caring SOPs and resources, and anticipation of grief. Being socialized by the hospice home care team, the family caregivers learn how to control symptoms beyond the basic techniques. While caring for the dying patients, the family caregivers arrange home space and medical devices, like an electric bed, mucus suction pump, oxygen concentrator. As anticipating the patient's disease progress, the family caregivers deploy affective labor while caring for them. This paper reveals that the practice of hospice home care does not merely depend on the patient's will but the family caregivers' work which is relatively invisible under the health insurance system.

Doing Research – Doing Care: Training Digital Skills for Nursing Education in a Transdisciplinary Project *Petra Lucht, Technische Universität Berlin; Sahra Dornick, Technical University Berlin; Heike Wiesner, Hochschule für*

Wirtschaft und Recht (HWR Berlin); Ute Kalender, FrauenComputerZentrumBerlin e.V. (FCZB), Berlin; Judith Schütze, Hochschule für Wirtschaft und Recht (HWR Berlin); Sandra Tausch, Technische Universität Berlin; Judith Holz, Technische Universität Berlin

In our paper, we deal with the question how ethnographers do care about and for collaborators, stakeholders, funders, careers and incomes, and commitments to justice at all stages of collaborative and transdisciplinary research. We provide insights into the joint research project "Digital Academy Care 4.0". This participatory research project pursues the goal of enabling teachers, practical instructors and student caregivers nationwide to create digital teaching and learning scenarios for generalist care apprenticeship, thus enabling individualised learning and the development of digital media competence in view of future requirements. In particular, the heterogeneity of learners (e.g. in terms of education, age, gender) and of teachers (e.g. in terms of digital literacy) is addressed. These target groups are included into a "community of practice" in the participatory development of digital media for blended learning environments. Consequently, changes in the learning culture in care apprenticeship are taking place in order to take into account the needs of nursing students* and teachers. The joint project is developing an "On the Job" coaching offer for these transformation processes. In this way, teachers in care apprenticeship will be supported in acquiring skills for the handling and the use of digital technologies and tools. In order to consolidate and disseminate the project results, an online platform will be developed and set up during the project. The project "DAPF 4.0 - Digital Academy care 4.0: Digital skills for generalist nursing education and training" (05/2020 – 04/2023) is funded by the Federal Ministry of Education and Research, funding no. 01PG20004

Equity as a Vector of Transdisciplinarity: The case of the Loricorps, a transdisciplinary laboratory studying eating disorders *Audrey Groleau, Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières; Johana Monthey-Blanc, Université du Québec à Trois-Rivières*

The Loricorps is a Canadian transdisciplinary research laboratory aiming to become a leader in eHealth interventions with patients living with eating disorders. Its members are educators, nurses, occupational therapists, psychologists, dieticians, etc. They work across and beyond several disciplines; transcending disciplinary boundaries through integrated management without hierarchy. We conducted a study on how Loricorps members view expertise – their own, the expertise of the other members of the laboratory and the expertise of the laboratory as a whole – and transdisciplinarity. Twelve members of the laboratory took part in semi-structured individual interviews that lasted from 30 to 60 minutes. The interviews were transcribed textually and qualitatively analyzed through analytical questioning. During the interviews, participants explained how they learned transdisciplinarity through four steps at their arrival in the laboratory. Once members of the laboratory take ownership of transdisciplinarity, they begin to introduce themselves through their disciplinary, transdisciplinary and non-disciplinary expertise instead of through their disciplines. They also recognize that those various types of expertise are essential to transdisciplinary work, whether they are individual or collective types of expertise. In a nutshell, the transdisciplinary and equity basic posture of the laboratory tints the way its new members take ownership of integrated work, which helps create an individual and collective expertise, which in turn reinforces the basic posture of the laboratory. These results and interpretations are further discussed during this communication.

Taking Care While Making Knowledge: Reflections of an Ethnographer Running a Syringe Exchange Program *Taylor Parrott, Southern Tier AIDS Program*

Trained to do STS ethnographically, I left a PhD program to help run a syringe exchange--enacting a so-called harm reduction response to illegal drug use. Harm reduction focus on the effects--rather than the act--of drug use and understand drug-related harms as contextual, social, and systemic. My STS work focuses on questions like: How do assumptions about risk undergird truth claims about and policy responses to addiction and addicts? How do care and control relate to each other? Studying harm reduction while doing it foregrounds another question: When we do research on and with people, especially those living in conditions of "everyday trauma" (Bourgeois & Schonberg, 2009), how do/can/should we care for them? Doing this work as an STSer, I am increasingly reckoning with the unavoidably fuzzy boundaries: I simultaneously study, provide care, and engage in myriad other ways at scales ranging from the individual to the community, and often beyond (Knight, 2015). I both engage in intentional care interventions and in emergent care relationships while working to produce and mobilize specific kinds of knowledge claims. I'm interested in using this panel to interrogate my fuzzily-defined practitioner-researcher position and the sometimes conflicting commitments and abilities that go along with it. I want to put my STS and harm reduction experiences into conversation with each other and with other scholars to explore what the future of care-full research can and should look like.

Session Organizers:

Caitlin Donahue Wylie, University of Virginia
Coleen Carrigan, California Polytechnic State University
Ute Kalender, FrauenComputerZentrumBerlin e.V. (FCZB), Berlin

572. STS Pedagogies Meet Up

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 20

What constitutes 'STS' pedagogy? Recognizing that STS scholars and teachers get their own training in a variety of disciplines, and then frequently move into yet other disciplines, STS pedagogies are often highly contextualized and innovative practices. At the same time, many STSers find themselves developing their pedagogies in relative isolation from other STS colleagues. Whether STS pedagogies occur in STS or STEM, an undergraduate or graduate level, a university or a museum, in particular national contexts or across borders, examining together how STS approaches teaching and learning provides opportunities for personal and intellectual support as well as collaboration. Centering STS pedagogies as sites of theorization and critical participation also invites us to interrogate STS commitments, objectives, and relations with the world. This meet-up is for all who are interested in STS pedagogies. Let's think together, share resources, and learn from each other.

Session Organizer:

Emily York, James Madison University

Chair:

Emily York, James Madison University

573. The Imposter as Engine of Uncertainty - III

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 21

Participants:

A Queer Test for Straight Imposters: The Polygraph's Sexual Politics *Jessa Lingel, University of Pennsylvania, Annenberg School for Communication*

The polygraph is arguably the most famous technology for detecting and evaluating imposters, with a century-long history of claiming to detect fact from fiction, pretenders from truth-tellers. Although the psychological validity of the polygraph has been contested almost since the technology's inception, it continues to enjoy substantial popularity in the U.S. among law enforcement and federal agencies. Among the many targets and objectives of the polygraph is an embedded history of

disciplining queer and marginalized bodies and desires. This paper excavates the sexual politics of the polygraph, focused on two key arenas where the polygraph remains a popular and powerful tool: screening employees in federal agencies and determining parole among sex offenders. Drawing on theories of technological spectacle, affect and queer use, this paper investigates the sexual politics of the polygraph machine. Key questions guiding my analysis include: how are queer bodies imagined by the polygraph's developers and examiners? How have queer bodies and desires been disciplined by the polygraph? And how does the polygraph fit within a larger history of surveilling and controlling sexual otherness?

Exposing academic imposter methods and precarious worlds
Jacob Nielsen, Robert Gordon University

What implications does it have for social theory when academic imposter techniques, performances and methods are revealed and made visible? This paper will explore this issue by building on the second part of my PhD thesis that sought to expose some of the imposter methods I utilised to build up a sense of analytical coherence and academic ability in the first part of my thesis on precarious work and living. The notion of academic imposters has mostly been used as a conceptual tool to uncover how a neoliberal social order have created increasingly precarious academic practices and patterns of social inequality. However, drawing on Law's (2004) work on the mess in method assemblages and Butler's (2009) work on precariousness as interdependence and vulnerability this paper seeks to explore how imposter practices and methods can be used to move towards other ways of apprehending precarious worlds. It will deliberate on how my eagerness to pass as a proper academic resulted in attempts to portray my analysis on precariousness as convincing and analytically robust. However, it will seek to reveal how the imposter methods I used to cover-up how my analysis and methodological practices were always unsettled, multiple, diverse, and interdependent on a range of social material factors ranging from academic feedback to the singular ordering performance of MS Word. Rather than shying away from this revelation I will discuss exposing these imposter methods can move towards precarious apprehensions that are more incomplete, contradictory, and vulnerable to the sway of others.

Maleness as a disruptive force in the field of eating disorders.
Piotr Maron, University of New South Wales

There is a common consensus that male eating disorders are under-researched and has been overlooked in research for a long time. The biomedical and epidemiological literature for many years now maintains that MEDs are 'on the rise', cases volume is considerably growing, and statistically, the disorder presents more and more severe risks. The starting point of this presentation is that the 'maleness' in eating disorders (ED) constitutes an ontological disturbance, an interruption, a thinking otherwise in relation to 'the standard' – female EDs. Based on 25 qualitative interviews with health care professionals working in the field of eating disorders, this paper conceptualizes maleness in eating disorder as a disruption in ways that eating disorders have been attended, managed and approached. In the presentation, I will show how maleness disrupts the order, facilitates disorder and uncertainty to explore its specific ontological registers. The paper will conclude what such a framework can offer in thinking about male eating disorders and how health care providers could benefit from it.

Session Organizers:

Else Vogel, University of Amsterdam - AISSR
David Moats, Linköping University, Tema-T (Tema Technology and Social Change)
Claes-Fredrik Helgesson, Centre for Integrated Research on Culture and Society (CIRCUS)

Chair:

Steve Woolgar, Linköping University

574. Technologies of Policing; Policing as Technology – III

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 22

Policing has always relied on technologies to assist in the spatial management and social control of populations. Recently, digital technologies have become increasingly central to police operations, which parallels a shift to more proactive forms of policing. Predictive policing, online surveillance, biometrics, facial recognition, machine learning, body cameras, gunshot detection, interoperable databases, and drones connect to existing police technologies as many departments attempt to shift to 'intelligence-led' or 'data-driven' approaches. With the current public crisis facing policing, there has been a growing questioning of the effects of technologies, computation, and data on practices of policing. How can STS approaches contribute to studying policing in its situated contexts, considering the uneven and often fraught implementation of technology? Given how little we know about what technologies of policing, or even policing as a technology itself can do, we invite perspectives and approaches that study the material impacts of policing. In this panel, we seek to include a diverse set of concerns and methods in order to reveal new depths and breadth to our understanding of how technologies of policing and policing as technology function and transform each other. These might include theoretical, methodological, or empirical contributions that, for example, historicize policing technologies (Jefferson, 2020); engage ethnographically with police officers, departments, or technology developers (Brayne, 2017); experiment with policing algorithms (Lum & Isaac, 2016); and more. Further, given the disproportionate use of violence against marginalized members of our communities, we encourage approaches that consider how to center resistive and abolitionist approaches in studying policing. Nick Lally (University of Kentucky) Xerxes Minocher (University of Wisconsin–Madison)

Participants:

Expecting the Future: Emerging Narratives on Automated Facial and Emotion Recognition Technologies. *Diana Miranda, University of Stirling; Lachlan David Urquhart, University of Edinburgh*

In this qualitative study, we explore UK police force perspectives on use of automated facial recognition (AFR) technologies. We consider the narratives of front line officers (26 semi-structured interviews) on how AFR would impact their professional practice. We observed scepticism and disbelief from officers around reliability, accuracy and effectiveness of AFR. Surprisingly, this often corresponds with wider critiques observed in the narratives around AFR from societal stakeholders including mass media, citizens and civil liberty groups. However, this scepticism fades as officers consider the future for AFR, where optimism and increased confidence in its use grows. We utilise literature from the 'sociology of expectations' (Borup et al, 2006; Brown et al, 2000) to complement our criminological and legal analysis that reflects on how these future visions shape potential use of AFR in UK policing. We also consider the related technique of emotion recognition that seeks to augment AFR by reading citizens emotive states. As an emergent tool, we draw on experiences from AFR to reflect on possible futures and expectations for this technology in policing too. Borup et al (2006) *Sociology of Expectations in Science and Technology. Technology Analysis and Strategic Management* 18:3-4. 285-298 N. Brown, B. Rappert & A. Webster (Eds), *Contested Futures: A Sociology of Prospective Techno-Science* (Aldershot, UK, Ashgate, 2000).

Between Pencils and Genetic Markers: On Forensic DNA Phenotyping and Facial Composite Drawing in Policing
Roos Hopman, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research, University of Amsterdam; Rianne Bleumink, Amsterdam Institute for Social Science Research, University of Amsterdam

To engage the public in a criminal investigation and as such

generate new leads, investigators may choose to circulate a facial composite image of an unknown suspect. In this paper we pause with the generation and distribution of such composite faces in policing. Comparing facial composite drawing to facial composites generated using DNA traces, we complicate the distinction between ‘low-tech’ and ‘high-tech’ forms of policing. We show that while there are clear differences between the two technologies, they work by a similar operational logic. Facial composite drawings are intentionally kept generic (contours are smudged, faces are preferably drawn in black-and-white) and often perceived as subjective and erroneous, while DNA ‘snapshots’ are presented as scientific and highly specific (facial characteristics are drawn out in great detail, faces are produced in full color). Yet in both technologies it is precisely the openness of the face that constitutes its virtue: through both the drawn and the ‘DNA-based’ faces the public is engaged in an investigation and as such enlisted in the work of policing. It is furthermore through this engagement that racializing effects may be produced. Drawing on ethnographic fieldwork conducted at the Dutch police, forensic genetic laboratories, and interviews with investigators and geneticists, we mobilize theories grounded in STS to demonstrate the differing (racializing) effects of technologically mediated faces in practice. In doing so, we furthermore add practical nuance to the STS scholarship on the face and race in forensic technologies.

#Instacops - Image, aesthetics and (self)representation of policing in the digital space: The Case of the Lower Saxony State Police on Instagram. *Alexa Agoropoulos, University of Hamburg; Ben Hundertmark, University of Hamburg; Tabea Louis*

Using the hashtag Instacops, German police officers from Lower Saxony State Police report on their everyday lives on official accounts on Instagram and engage through the production of images in the aesthetic (self)representations of police institutions. This new personalized communication strategy follows the concept of Digital Community Policing, which aims to increase citizens "openness, sensitivity and trust" towards the police and to expand the institutional presence into the digital space. The visual references produced in the process relate to already existing (digital) communities and social media cultures, which in turn shape the aesthetic image of police officers' content on Instagram as a kind of echo-effect. The platform provides a fruitful environment for community-building with other emergency services and empowers the connection to contemporary digital media cultures and communities, who have previously not been in touch with the police community or official social media output of the police itself. Based on an in-depth visual² and intertextual³ analysis of selected posts as well as semi-structured interviews⁴ with social media managers and police officers from Lower Saxony State Police, who perform as Digital Community Policers, we argue that the algorithmic and social logics of Instagram favor the production of a specific type of "security" through digital image work and (self)representation of police actors: Through the production of visual and intertextual narratives of contemporary policing, the police address digital communities on Instagram by drawing on platform specific influencer marketing strategies and personalized branding. Instacops become personalities who promote a positive self-image of their organizational brand and, by the visually generated trust, coproducing a certain feeling of safety. As we intend to illustrate, a favorable image of the police subsequently becomes synonymous for security itself.

On the modularity of predictive policing *Nick Lally, University of Kentucky*

The increasing use of data and software by police departments has become a matter of concern for scholars, especially in light of growing social movements protesting the structural racism and violence of policing in the U.S.. While many studies highlight the

problems with using police data in predictive policing software, fewer have shown how such technologies are received and used in their situated contexts. Based on interviews with developers of predictive policing software and informed by STS studies of technologies in use, I show how developers navigate translations between their data models and policing practices. These translations, I argue, are fraught as developers are isolated from the concrete practices that their software attempts to transform. As a result, I conceptualize predictive policing as a modular technology that is plugged into the black box of policing. In this talk, I highlight three implications for understanding software and policing that emerge from the separation between developers and police. First, modularity means that predictive policing can be sold on a model of deterrence—a vision that is at odds with policing as it is actually practiced. Second, modularity allows developers to strategically distance themselves from the most oppressive practices of policing. And third, modularity means that software can be adopted, reconfigured, and misused in ways that are at odds with its original intent, producing concerning assemblages of data, surveillance technologies, and predictive software.

Session Organizer:

Nick Lally, University of Kentucky

Chair:

Xerxes Minocher, University of Wisconsin-Madison

575. Theatre of Negotiations

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 23

Participant:

The Theatre of Negotiations *Hsin-Hsing Chen, Shih-Hsin University Graduate Institute for Social Transformation Studies*

The “Theater of Negotiations” is a practical implementation of the “political and diplomatic tactics” that inform the Taipei Biennial 2020. The program content is a collaboration among researchers from the Taiwan STS Association and students from five universities to engage in role-playing while addressing several social controversies that exist in Taiwan today. These range from climate emergency to nuclear waste, food safety, renewable energy, and assisted conception. The role-playing takes the form of debates about these controversies, with participants representing the various stakeholders (lobbyists, judges, NGOs, local politicians, residents, and non-human actors etc.), engaging in realistic exercises in negotiation and public governance of the issue in question.

Session Organizer:

Hsin-Hsing Chen, Shih-Hsin University Graduate Institute for Social Transformation Studies

576. Kerala Relations: Gender, Digital, and Agricultural Equality in the "Model" State

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 3

Perhaps no part of the planet is prouder but more uncertain about its equality than Kerala, the South Indian state known for its unique "model" in which social development is relatively high, while economic development is moderate to low. In spheres such as digital literacy, gender relations, and agriculture, progressive programs have been promoted under a variety of governments. Universal literacy and health care are widely supported and even advertised as goals that have been achieved. This session examines current conditions in several areas as well as the extent to which programs reduce or exacerbate inequalities.

Participants:

Engendering Gender Relations Technology of Power and Sexuality among Nayars in Kerala, South India *Lekha N B, Sree Narayana College, Chempazhanthy*

Unlike most regions in India, Kerala had a history of an open discourse on sexuality due to the glorified matrilineal system. Matrilineal system existed in Kerala even during the nineteenth and twentieth centuries. Sexuality, prompted by the socially constructed and culturally coded existence of the female body, provides space for its transformation by changing those aspects of the socially and culturally constructed bodies. The marumakkattayam (matrilineal kinship) system of Nayars in Kerala conferred special rights on women with regard to sexuality and property. This has been effectuated by the features of matrilineality which had an impact on women's situation, namely, inheritance and descent through the female line, joint family form of living wherein women had a definite position, absence of 'marriage' and 'fatherhood', property rights in the name of the woman and right over children belonging to the mother's family. However, changes in social conditions due to colonialism, brought about by notions of progress rendered these rights 'immoral' and 'primitive'. Here I focus on how the imposition of power through legislative measures and colonial ideology changed values with regards to marriage and family subsequently to the sexuality of Nayar women.

Has the Internet Reduced Gender Inequality in Science? A Test of the Circumvention Thesis in Kerala, Ghana, and Kenya
Paige Miller, University of Wisconsin, River Falls; Wesley Shrum, Louisiana State University

At the turn of the 21st century, some argued that ICTs had the potential to alter the very social structure of science. This potential for social change was argued by some to be particularly relevant for the careers of women in low-income areas who, the available studies suggested, traveled less than men for research, training, or educational purposes, published less in international journals, and reported smaller professional networks. Some theorized women's more local orientation to their career had the effect of restricting their opportunities to meet, share information and collaborate with nonlocal others, ultimately weakening their publication productivity, particularly in foreign venues. Coined the circumvention thesis, it was theorized that the very nature of online activity might provide women the means to subvert—or circumvent—gendered norms impeding their careers. We address the circumvention argument through the use of longitudinal survey data gathered from a sample of academics and researchers working in Ghana, Kenya, and Kerala, India. Five questions are asked reflecting the findings of a core set of earlier studies exploring the circumvention thesis. First, we ask to what extent female researchers continue to exhibit a more local orientation to their careers both in comparison to men and overtime. Second, has the dramatic increase in access to personal computers and email noted in earlier studies continued? Third, does there appear to be a relationship between women's access to ICTs and the number of professional ties they report? Fourth, do any changes in access to ICTs and professional ties co-vary with changes in publication patterns such that gender differences on these measures are not apparent? And finally, to what extent does country context matter in shaping careers?

Industrial Vs. Organic Agriculture: Signals of A Subaltern Civil Society in Kerala, India
Antony Palackal, University of Kerala, Kariyavattom Campus

The paper seeks to examine the current organic boom in the state as a response to the impending agrarian crisis and issues of food security, food price and health in the state of Kerala, a developing region in India. It employs a political ecology perspective from the margins, as it is grounded in the concerns about the struggles over natural resources and the livelihoods of people within the context of post capitalist mode of production in a liberalized economy. Situating the problematic within the conceptual frame of 'risk society', the Polanyan notion of countermovement (1944) is employed to unearth the Kerala's agrarian crisis of the 1990s that stemmed up from the

commodification of agriculture, which ultimately led to an ecological countermovement in the form of organic farming in the early twenty first century. On the basis of the field data, it is argued that organic agriculture from the marginal farmers emerges as an agrarian counter discourse against the dominant discourse of the market-driven agrarian economy, which is likely to shape into a radical form of state-led development and politics with the input of a subaltern civil society in the State.

Digital Inclusion and Developmental Paradox – The Case of A Developing Region
Wesley Shrum, Louisiana State University; Antony Palackal, University of Kerala, Kariyavattom Campus

In a ubiquitous information and communication environment, with the new developments in digital technologies, individuals tend to increasingly engage in digital communication, collaboration, information and social networking, which have become integral part of the everyday life in contemporary society. In the past several years, there have been waves of digital initiatives, particularly in developing nations, to harness and enhance the developmental and transformative power of digital media. The study presents the influence of the socio-cultural factors in determining the use and access to digital technologies and media for digital inclusion in a developing region. It unravels the case of Kerala in the Indian subcontinent, known for its unique developmental model that showed high social development on a weak economic basis. Based on the data collected from areas of impoverished households in certain poverty pockets, the study examines the use and access to digital technologies and media in a State that pioneered digital communication and information policy in India two decades ago.

Session Organizer:

Matthew Harsh, California Polytechnic State University

Chair:

Wesley Shrum, Louisiana State University

Discussant:

Mark J Joseph Schafer, LSU AgCenter

577. Ecologies of Empire II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 5

This panel offers ecologies of empire as a frame within which to detect state efforts to territorialize and materialize sovereign power through extensive biotic and geologic systems across space and time. We attend to practices and legacies of war, colonization, and enslavement by exploring the extensive choreography of uneven human and more-than-human flourishing and ruination engendered in land, water, air, waste, and flesh, both by design, and also through practiced ignorance. We understand ecologies here as natural-cultural spaces-entangled materialities that make living and dying possible-asserting that both an anthropocentric scale and the specific frictions of empire remain integral to any ecological scene. By bringing together work in and on both centers and peripheries of empire (US, Puerto Rico, Korea, India, Iraq), we seek to find new ways to put these nodes into relation. This includes attending to displaced violences, both fast and slow, externalized and internalized, that redistribute the possibilities of living and dying across emergent ecological niches. We also ask what it means to make good relations both to and within our ecologies, as well as to each other as scholars with overlapping but distinct formations and localizations of empire. We aim to convene these varied projects under the sign of allyship, rather than through a logic of scholarly extraction (how does your work serve my project), and take the occasion of the panel to manifest forms of scholarly conviviality, through parallel practices such as the creation of a collaborative panel playlist and optional co-writing sessions.

Participants:

Surviving the Hunt: White-Tailed Deer on Culebra Island and Reciprocal Capture on the Edges of Empire
Adriana Maria Garriga-López, Kalamazoo College

While White-Tailed deer are not endemic to Puerto Rico, I discuss how they have adapted to the tropical ecosystem in the aftermath of the US naval occupation of Culebra without appearing to cause significant ecological disruption. Brought to Culebra as game in the early 20th century by US American sailors stationed at the now-closed naval base that once dominated life on the island, the deer are a living, though spectral remnant of US colonial (de)militarization. Although live fire exercises and bombing practice at the Culebra Naval Base range ended in 1975, the US Navy has since refused to remediate the environmental damage caused by these exercises, merely designating the former firing ranges as Wildlife Refuge areas and leaving in situ the slowly decomposing detritus of war. The descendants of animals brought from North America to the Caribbean as captives and then either abandoned by soldiers or escaped from these military installations, Culebra's White-Tailed deer have also captured the affections and imaginations of Puerto Ricans, who generally see them as benign and do not hunt them. I argue that in the afterlife of (de)militarization, humans and deer on Culebra are engaged in a 'grasping together' of the future; a form of reciprocal capture that forges new ecologies and new, multi-species ecological epistemologies. I posit that the deer are rendered as fugitive rather than as invasive species by Puerto Ricans and other humans living in and visiting Culebra. The stakes of survival for both species are different, yet interconnected.

Rural Black Social Life in the Chesapeake After the 1933 Great Hurricane *J.T. Roane, Arizona State University*

This talk draws from work on the post-1933 history of rural Tidewater communities in Virginia through the prism of Black ecologies. Since the colonial period, Black life in the region has been delimited by shifting regimes of extraction, disaccumulation (Gilmore) and enclosure. Following more than a decade of agricultural decline and resulting Black land loss in the 1920s, the area was struck by the Great Hurricane of 1933 which destroyed the region's wharf infrastructure. Although already endangered by increasing rural automobility and the dislocation of agricultural modes of life due to land loss and rural displacement, the final dissolution of the wharf system transformed the social-ecological terrain of Black life, giving rise to increasingly "urbanized" rural Black life and leisure cultures. As Carter G. Woodson documents, the emergence of urbanized rural Black culture marked the shifting cultural terrain of consolidation of the segregated commercial amusements and Black self-creation in the context of rural reterritorialization. I engage Black cultural texts produced in and about the region, including a recorded rag guitar performance, work songs, and other contemporary cultural productions. Although these forms lack credibility within the dominant regimes of ecological thought privileging management and a horizon of future extraction, they nevertheless index the critical ecological resources produced in Black expressive culture that map and make sense of the unique ecotone outside the paradigm of ownership and extraction.

What happens when war is what queers an ecology? *Kali Rubaii, Purdue University*

Queer theory is integral to liberative political projects because it is about denaturalizing norms, or refuting biological justifications for hierarchy. But, in a war ecology, hierarchies among humans and their plant or animal crops, women and sexual reproduction, and human bodies in/over their environments, are deconstructed not by critical resistance from below or by transformative grassroots mobilization, but instead by the coercive regimes of war and empire. What does it mean when the presence of transgender fish in the Tigris or the prevalence of infertility among women in Fallujah signals toxicity and harm, rather than biodiversity that support human claims for gender inclusive equality? What does it mean for queer theory when, instead of choosing to distinguish sexuality from reproduction, women are

forced to do so by physical violence upon their bodies; or when anomalies in living bodies do the work of holding corporate polluters accountable, but could also undermine discourse demonstrating the naturalness of "anomaly"?

Body Heat: Race, Climate and the Consolidation of Imperial Difference *Bharat Jayram Venkat, UCLA*

As Montesquieu put it in his Spirit of Laws (1750), "The empire of the climate is the first, the most powerful of all empires." Rather than simply a statement in support of climatic determinism, we might read his claim as gesturing toward the centrality of climate to the consolidation and maintenance of imperial power. Focusing on late 19th and early 20th century India, this talk explores how heat and light, as related but distinct phenomena, were conceptualized as entering into and altering different kinds of racialized bodies and populations -- and in fact, producing such racialization. Thinking through the work of colonial physicians, meteorologists, and administrators, as well as architects and clothiers, this talk attends to the ways in which the "Indian sun" became a critical figure for conceptualizing and responding to racialized, embodied forms of difference. What I will argue, then, is that British colonial power depended on a deeply ecological conception of the body, while detailing how precisely such an ecology was both imagined and actively transformed.

Session Organizers:

Zoe Wool, University of Toronto
Xan Sarah Chacko, Wellesley College

Chair:

Zoe Wool, University of Toronto

Discussant:

Hilei Hobart, The University of Texas at Austin

578. Emergence in Environmental Infrastructures - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 6

Participants:

Infrastructural Affects and Emergence in the Making of a Moroccan Anthropocene *Daniel Williford, University of Wisconsin*

The concept of emergence calls attention to the ways that built infrastructures are bound together not just by pipes and wires but through forms of affect and enjoyment. Centered around two scenes from Morocco's post-independence history, this talk considers how the emergence of infrastructures with critical environmental impacts has been interwoven with nationalist "socio-technical imaginaries" (Kim and Jasanoff 2015) of development and decolonization. I consider the recent construction of the Noor Solar Power Station near Ouarzazate alongside the post-independence history of Morocco's largest cement plant in Casablanca. Both the power station and the plant were sites where grand national visions of development encountered the messy realities of conflicts over land and labor. While each project took a distinct approach to extraction and accumulation, they differed primarily in the forms of affect and enjoyment that they sought to engender in workers, residents, and consumers. Cement and solar energy appear to occupy opposing ends of the spectrum in contemporary discussions of climate change and environmental engineering. In Morocco, however, both are intertwined with the emergence of infrastructures designed to produce and harness desires for development. Drawing on oral histories with former cement plant workers and accounts of displacement for the sake of solar power, this talk deploys the concept of emergence to call attention not only to the effects but also to the affects of environmental infrastructures. In the process, I reflect on how to tell stories about the Anthropocene that center desire, enjoyment, and affect alongside questions of extraction and inequality.

Infrastructural Limbo: Managing Municipal Waste in Small Town Settings *Aarti Latkar; Aalok Khandekar, Indian Institute of Technology Hyderabad*

This ethnographic research focuses on the municipal waste infrastructure for solid waste management in a small town in southern India which has experienced significant growth in recent years. Building on the anthropology of infrastructure and waste, we detail this town's sustained and ongoing struggles to find a place to dump and process its waste. The continual production of waste implies that the municipal infrastructure for waste management must continue to function despite its inadequacies, while additionally also struggling to conform to regulatory guidelines issued by various state agencies for proper waste disposal. We use the term 'limbo' to refer to these conditions of seemingly perpetual uncertainties, indecisions and transience that come to define infrastructural arrangements in such a case. This paper highlights the characteristics of a growing town that allow for and create such conditions—spatially, politically, administratively—for it to be caught in an infrastructural limbo. It also draws out the changing tactics that municipal officials and workers devise in order to cope with such uncertainties on an everyday basis. The contributions of this paper are three-fold: first, to the predominantly urban-centric focus of the anthropology of infrastructure, it presents an empirical analysis at the scale of a small town. Second, it questions the environmental, social, and other effects that conditions of limbo produce. Third, more generally, as a growing number of smaller towns experience urbanisation, the analysis offers ways to think through the opportunities and challenges that such processes present in India and globally.

Interplanetary Infrastructures in the Search for Evidence of Life *Dana Burton, George Washington University*

If all goes according to plan, by the 2030s, samples of martian soil will be brought back to Earth. Despite the optimism of this NASA announcement, the current Mars Sample Return (MSR) mission that began with the landing of Perseverance Rover on February 18, 2021, is only the latest effort to acquire martian samples. The possibility of MSR really happening this time has mobilized NASA to re-investigate the consequences of bringing earthly and (potentially) martian life into proximity. As scientists dig into the foundations of biological transmissibility, through such activities as revisiting sample quarantine facility schematics to reorganizing the Office of Planetary Protection's contamination control policies, it unearths multiple complex histories of desires to understand the fundamentality of life as well as deploy technoscientific knowledge to do so. Combining archival research on the various iterations of MSR over the last 70 years with ethnographic fieldwork of current MSR development strategies, I explore scientists' efforts to be accountable for interplanetary research as nodes of emergence. In these nodes, each intra-action (Barad 2007) of MSR across spatial and temporal dimensions assembles ecologies of knowledges (Rahder 2020) that both support and alter the infrastructures of the Mars exploration program and astrobiology as a science. In this paper, I follow the current reverberations of MSR discussions and how they connect multiple entities (both human and nonhuman) to understand the space that opens around the mission's "core" purpose – to search for evidence of life. What can be learned about the mechanisms that produce scientific knowledge about life by attending to the scaffolding of adjacent interests to this astrobiological endeavor? Citations: Barad, Karen. 2007. *Meeting the Universe Halfway: Quantum Physics and the Entanglement of Matter and Meaning*. Durham: Duke University Press. Rahder, Micha. 2020. *An Ecology of Knowledges: Fear, Love, and Technoscience in Guatemalan Forest Conservation*. Durham: Duke University Press.

Of Dams and Goats: Emergent Ecologies at Infrastructural Sites *Ekin Kurtic, Brandeis University*

The body of a dead wild goat floating upside down in a dam reservoir manifests the infrastructural violence more-than-human entities are subjected to as a result of the enclosure of river waters. The excitement of an engineer sitting in front of his temporary container house at a large dam construction site in seeing a wild goat family descending the hill to drink water from the river shows a relation of care that takes place alongside the practice of taming the river. A group of goats climbing up a dam wall to lick off the water dissolving the salt and minerals contained in the rock demonstrates the unplanned utilization of infrastructures by more-than-humans. Each of these three instances of animal-infrastructure entanglement sheds light on the limits of dams in simply conquering the landscapes and imposing technical control over "unruly nature." This paper attends to emergent and messy ecologies of violence, care, and use beyond the neatly designed blueprints of environmental infrastructures. By tracing the unexpected movements and appearances of goats in dammed landscapes, this paper shows that technical infrastructures are environmentally embedded entities, whose construction and operation processes are bound up with emergent multispecies relations embodying divergent forms of ecocide, intimacy, and repurposing.

Session Organizer:

Akshita Sivakumar, University of California at San Diego

579. Financializing climate and climatizing finance - II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 7

This session seeks contributions that use STS and related concepts and frameworks to study the range of efforts to align financial flows with the composition of the atmosphere and its effects on climate. This involves developing climate metrics, translating them to financial terms, and bringing them to bear on investment calculations. We expect the many mediations between the realms of finance and climate to be sites of contention and uncertainty, providing openings for a range of STS research traditions: the study of metrics, standards, and commensuration; the construction of calculating agents through devices and calculative practices; assetization and commodification of the natural world; risk. Here's a partial listing of possible questions: • What is left outside the frame when the climate problem is translated to terms of a homogeneous medium of exchange? • To what extent are financial practices part of a socio-technical regime that resists change? • What processes and actors shape the mediations between the atmosphere's chemistry and the language of finance? And an equally partial listing of empirical objects that could fit comfortably within the session: • Renewable energy finance – techniques for mobilizing investment in renewable energy. • Climate risk measurement and disclosure – efforts to require firms to measure their exposure to climate risk and to disclose that risk. • Devaluation of fossil reserves – how fossil fuel producers devalue the volume and value of their reserves. • Climate finance technologies and devices – "Climate fintech" – analytic products and platforms and how they make a financial world that reflects climate impacts • Development, rating, verification, and valuation of carbon-free and ESG financial products.

Participants:

Electricity arbitrage: the emergence of a financial practice
Daniel Breslau, Virginia Tech

An electric power system based on renewable generation will require massive temporal decoupling of supply and demand of electricity, facilitated mostly by electricity storage technologies. In a financialized world, this calls for large-scale temporal arbitrage of electricity, in other words buying electric energy when it's cheap and selling it when it's expensive. Temporal arbitrage in electricity is both a consequence of the growth of electric storage capacity and a precondition for investment in storage capacity; investment in storage won't take place on the needed scale unless arbitrage can promise returns on that investment. This paper employs conceptual and methodological tools from social studies of finance, STS, and economic sociology, to analyze electric energy arbitrage as emerging

financial practice. The electricity arbitrager and her calculative practices depend on a novel assemblage. It includes the development of software platforms to support arbitrage; mathematical algorithms developed by economists and engineers to optimize arbitrage based on analysis and forecasts of entire power systems; new market rules and regulations for the participation of storage in electricity markets; and a general reconceptualization of the product from electric power as a flow to electric energy as a stock. Finally, the paper examines the failure to date of electricity arbitrage to attract investment in storage that will allow countries to reach their clean energy targets.

Reconfiguring Energy for Post-Covid-19 Development *Jesse Hoffman, Urban Futures Studio / Utrecht University; Megan Davies, Stellenbosch University*

The socio-economic and political crisis triggered by the COVID-19 pandemic has shifted the position and mandate of financial institutions, development finance institutions (DFIs) in particular. For these institutions, the resulting crisis is interrupting business-as-usual and forcing a break with many old “truths” and conventions in policymaking. Whereas DFIs were previously readjusting their role vis-a-vis the tremendous challenge of financing the energy transition, they now become key to financing post-COVID-19 recovery. This raises the question as to whether investments in renewable energy, together with other forms of climate action, can become a driver in for post-crisis recovery. Contributing to this, this paper aims to develop a analytical framework on the relationship between the positioning of DFIs in post-crisis recovery and the potential re-aligning of investments in renewable energy, with other developmental objectives such as health, economic recovery, and ameliorating social inequities. Theoretically, the focus of this paper is on the techniques and practices of institutional work that restructure the allocation of funds aimed at post-COVID-19 recovery, and how this ‘recoding’ work may enable or constrain synergies across development and climate objectives. Empirically, this paper presents the first results of this consortium’s investigation into how funds for post-COVID-19 recovery are allocated, and in the process, how this might lead to adjustments in terms of: i) new visions for the future (re-imagination), ii) new rules of the game (re-coding), and iii) new technical and financial arrangements (re-configuration). These empirical findings are presented with reference to DFIs operating within diverse global contexts.

The Unruly Objects of Climate Insurance *Amiel Bize, Cornell University*

In the last decade, as part of a wider trend toward using financial products to address poverty, a new climate-sensitive insurance product called “index-based insurance” (IBI) has become a darling of development circles. Promoted heavily by the World Bank, IBI is marketed as increasing “resilience” among farmers and pastoralists facing climate change. Rather than operating like standard insurance, IBI uses a weather indicator to anticipate loss. If “triggered,” it pays out regardless of whether a loss actually happens. IBI is intriguing both at an epistemological and a socio-political level. On the one hand, it is a radical innovation within efforts to model and predict the likelihood of loss. It produces the environment as an object of actuarial and financial knowledge by selecting a single variable (the “index”) as a predictor of widespread degradation. On the other, it is part of a global effort to draw the rural poor into formal banking and credit systems by turning vulnerable populations into consumers of risk-based products. This paper examines a specific IBI product, livestock insurance currently being sold to pastoralists in East Africa. Tracking the introduction of this product in northern Kenya, the paper examines 1) how two unruly objects—“weather” and “cattle”—are converted into standardized data points, and 2) how the product has been received by communities organized around other systems of value and risk management. It considers how IBI works both as a way of knowing and as a

practical attempt to make pastoralists into bearers of financialized risk.

Tragedy of the Horizons. Carbon ontologies between climate governance and finance *Andreas Folkers, Justus-Liebig University Gießen*

In a widely recognized speech, Mark Carney, former governor of the Bank of England, argued that climate risks represent a „tragedy of the horizon“. There are insufficient incentives to properly deal with climate change, because its effects will be felt only after it is already too late. However, a closer look reveals that financial climate risks not only represent a tragedy of one horizon, but a tragedy of plural and intersecting horizons. The presentation seeks to make sense of the multiplicity of (social) horizons of climate change. It looks at the way NGOs link climate change and financial markets by giving shape to and making up the so called “carbon bubble”: the ecologically and economically controversial problem that a consistent implementation of international climate goals could contribute to a massive devaluation of the financial assets of fossil capitalism. The presentation will unpack the steps of problematization by which unburnable fossil fuels become financial risks. It will focus on the many different calculative devices and infrastructures from both finance and climate science involved in this process. The presentation will argue that these calculative devices enact different carbon ontologies – carbon as greenhouse gas in climate science, carbon as regulated by climate governance, fossil fuels as assets on financial markets etc. – and will conclude that the temporal tragedy is an effect of the specific *Eigenzeiten* of the multiple carbon ontologies.

Session Organizer:

Daniel Breslau, Virginia Tech

580. From Hard Case to Fringe Interest: Mathematics and the Sociology of Science Reconsidered -- II

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 8

Mathematical Subjects and Geographies

Participants:

Women mathematicians in Chile: sociology of a scientific field from an interdisciplinary and gender perspective *Jeanne Hersant, Pontificia Universidad Católica de Chile; Fernando Valenzuela, Universidad Andres Bello*

We will present the first outcomes of an ongoing research project with a twofold purpose: 1) mapping the field of mathematics in order to define the dominant players and positions, as well as the networks that underlie these positions; 2) and a reconstruction of the career path of women mathematicians that shows the steps that women had to overcome to be inserted in this field. The year 2018 has witnessed in Chile an important social movement triggered mainly from the universities. In the present project we seek to give relevance to what feminist and gender perspectives imply for academic practice, and we do so from the study and reflection on an emblematic disciplinary field of the so-called ‘ivory tower’ of science, namely, mathematics. Studies that have addressed the low participation of women in mathematics have focused mainly on school education, suggesting that the relationship that girls have with mathematics is strongly conditioned by gender stereotypes. In this project, we will focus on women academics who are already inserted in the mathematical discipline as researchers. We conducted 10 mixed and women only focus groups and biographic interviews with 8 women (3 in-depth interviews with each). After a brief description of the mathematical field in Chile, we will in this presentation focus on these women’s biographical accounts in order to identify the common pattern of the career – according to Howard Becker’s concept – of female researchers in mathematics, namely the different stages one has to go through to reach the status of researcher.

Centering the Fringe: A Focus on Mathematical Knowledge across Fields and Contexts *Ellen Abrams, Cornell University; A. Feder Cooper, Cornell University*

Social and historical studies of mathematics are necessarily defined by the category itself. In the early-twentieth-century United States, the category “mathematician” shrank around those who pursued abstract, so-called “modern,” research. In the aftermath of World War II, a separate community of applied mathematicians developed around increasing opportunities in computer science and industry. Although such boundaries are neither stable nor well defined, they are important to consider for scholars who are interested in the social and historical production of mathematical knowledge. In this talk, we argue that the methods and interests that guide social and historical studies of mathematics can and ought to be applied more widely. In other words, there is potential to expand the analytical category “mathematician” and to find practicing mathematicians outside the traditional bounds of mathematics departments. Although studies of algebra and set theory should continue, there is ample opportunity to ask questions about the development of mathematics across a variety of applied fields where the mathematics is often overshadowed in science studies literature by the content and politics of the field itself. As an example, we will discuss our recent collaboration, as a historian of mathematics and computer scientist, in which we critiqued a subset of algorithmic fairness research. Unlike many studies of data and computing, we asked questions of the mathematics.

Crafting the "Oriental": Race and Minds in the History of Mathematics *Clare Kim*

STS scholars and historians of mathematics have increasingly appreciated the role of written practice and bodily perception in producing mathematical research. In treating the relationship between thought and symbolic formalisms, for instance, they now avoid reproducing notions of universal and disembodied cognition. Yet little attention has been paid to how notions of disembodied cognition came to be in the first place. This talk examines how historians of mathematics negotiated conceptualizations of race in their studies of symbolic formalisms and their imagined relation to cognition. In particular, I focus on the efforts of early twentieth-century mathematicians and historians to produce a history of Chinese and Japanese mathematics for an American readership. Analyzing their efforts to translate and categorize mathematics of the “Orient,” I show how their assertions of equating “Oriental” mathematics with the formalized axiomatic approach of the early 1900s depended upon treating mathematicians monolithically, without regard to changes and differences of racial ideology.

Mathematical Peripheries: Marginal Proofs and Marginal Identities in a Global Discipline *Michael J Barany, University of Edinburgh*

Of any science, mathematics ought to accommodate contributions from the social and geographical margins most easily. Mathematical knowledge is purportedly universal and self-contained, governed by rules of inference and validity accessible to anyone, anywhere. The mathematics discipline's twentieth-century globalization would appear at first glance to confirm the ready mobility of mathematics, but marginal identities and heterodox mathematics are not hard to find beneath the superficial harmonies of high theory. My presentation examines the production of mathematical marginality through two interwoven threads from the history and sociology of mathematics: rigor and validity as culturally contingent values particularly implicated in the marginalization of heterodox mathematics from South and East Asia from Srinivasa Ramanujan to Damodar Kosambi to Shinichi Mochizuki; and 'crackpot' proofs of famous theorems as race- and class-coded indices of center-periphery relationships in the archives of elite mathematical institutions. These converge in the most famous

marginal figure in the history of mathematics, the literally marginal claim and promised proof by Pierre de Fermat of the number-theoretical hypothesis that came to be called Fermat's Last Theorem.

Session Organizer:

Michael J Barany, University of Edinburgh

Discussant:

Massimo Mazzotti, University of California, Berkeley

581. Good Governance, Good Relations and (Nuclear) Waste Management IV

6:40 to 8:10 pm

4S 2021 Virtual: 9

Too often technical experts and government officials have seen the management and disposition of (nuclear) waste as a problem to be solved by experts, with the solution then “sold” to the broader public through techniques of public relations that are often so transparently manipulative as to be self-undermining. Instead of seeing waste management and disposition as narrowly technical problems to be resolved through techniques of quantitative risk assessment and cost-benefit analysis, they should be reframed as “wicked problems” (Churchman 1967, Rittel and Webber 1973) with the potential to disrupt good relations across a number of sociotechnical planes: between neighbors; between indigenous and settler populations; between corporations and local communities; between scientists and the public; and between state and society. Is it possible to solve these problems without toxic social consequences? We call on colleagues to draw on STS and the knowledge of its multiple ancillary disciplines to imagine sociotechnical processes that could build good social, political, and environmental relations. This might involve critique of existing processes, reportage of innovative improvements, or advocacy of novel processes. It will surely involve multi-perspectival visioning. Our primary interest is in nuclear waste, but we will entertain proposed papers on other waste forms as well.

Participants:

For the Love of the Danube: Nuclear Residues and Residual Affection *ELANA RESNICK, University of California, Santa Barbara*

Kozloduy, a town on the banks of the Danube River in northwestern Bulgaria, has become known for its Soviet-built nuclear power plant that during the socialist period supplied 44% of the country's energy and currently provides energy for about one third of Bulgaria's electricity needs. Environmental activists, power plant workers, and town residents differ in their understandings of the past and future of the plant, often citing their positionality in relation—or in opposition—to what they call “the Chernobyl story.” Despite their varying beliefs and histories, they overlap in their affective relationships to the river upon which the power plant is perched: the Danube. In this paper, I argue that the Danube River—and scientists', local residents', differently racialized workers', and activists' relationships with it—mediates technical processes of contamination remediation and nuclear decommissioning. Drawing on the idea of nuclear residue (Boudia et al. 2018), this paper explores how these different actors find commonality in their deep ties to the Danube River in order to position themselves in terms of both a Chernobyl-ridden past and a remediated future.

Human Beings as Nuclear Waste: Neoliberal Governance of Nuclear Medicine *Hugh Gusterson, University of British Columbia; Allison Macfarlane, George Washington University*

New cancer treatments use nuclear medicine to target tumors. For instance, thyroid and prostate cancers are now routinely treated by placing radioactive iodine-131 adjacent to the tumor. In most countries the patient is hospitalized until their radiation levels have fallen. In the profit-driven medical system in the United States, this is out-patient treatment, and highly radioactive

patients are routinely released with instructions on reducing radiation exposure to others, especially children. If such patients go home, they pose a hazard to family members. If they go to a hotel, they endanger those who clean their rooms. If they catch planes or buses, they expose fellow passengers sitting next to them. And many, financially insecure, will return to work before they should. The risk inherent in this situation, which turns individual human beings into waste disposal units, is largely invisible except for the people who regularly trigger radiation alarms at airports, sporting events and so on. This is a classically neoliberal approach to risk management in the way it prioritizes cost containment for institutions, externalizes the costs of compliance onto regular citizens, and places the onus on individuals to understand risk dynamics and behave responsibly. This risk needs to be made visible, retheorized as collective and systemic, and put under rigorous oversight.

Reimagining Radiation Protection: The Beaverlodge Cohort and Nuclear Regulation *Aaron Sidney Wright, Dalhousie University*

In 1978, a small group of employees at Eldorado Nuclear Ltd began an epidemiological project to study the health of workers in Eldorado's uranium mines, mills, and processing plants. Using company employment records, they constructed cohorts of mine and mill workers at sites including mines in the Beaverlodge area of Northern Saskatchewan. These mines made Canada the largest global uranium producer for much of the latter twentieth-century. The Beaverlodge cohort has also assumed international importance. It informs global standards for radiation protection produced by the US National Research Council and the United Nations. Susan Lindee recently emphasized the imaginative reenactments undertaken in Japanese cohort studies of radiation disasters. The decades-long occupational activities of the Beaverlodge miners have been similarly imagined and reimagined by a complex of industrial-medical-scientific actors. This presentation highlights the meaning of "radiation protection" engendered by these reimaginings, from 1981 to 2010. This institutional imagination was severely circumscribed. The cohort is a purified assembly of gendered (95% men) but deracinated bodies, meant for circulation within general assembly of international cohorts. According to company records, the cohort was exposed to Radon daughters in Northern Saskatchewan, but is overwhelmingly composed of bodies from elsewhere in Canada. Northern Saskatchewan is part of the traditional territory of the Dene, Cree, and Métis Indigenous peoples. In recent Canadian regulatory hearings about nuclear activities, waste "remediation," and the environment, Indigenous leaders have questioned, critiqued, and called for an improved radiation protection. This presentation juxtaposes the meaning of "radiation protection" produced by the Beaverlodge cohort with the imagined possibility of a different radiation protection.

Wasting Good Houses, Lands, and Relations: Missing Ethnographic Expertise in Decontamination of Coastal Fukushima *Ryo Morimoto, Princeton University*

This paper investigates the Japanese government's multi-billion-dollar decontamination project in coastal region of Fukushima prefecture and the twenty-two million cubic meters of low-level nuclear waste the project has subsequently produced. In the last ten years, decontamination simultaneously reduced the evacuation zone's size in Fukushima from 8 percent (1,150 km²) to 2.5 percent (370 km²) while destroying people's residences and farms, landscape, and ecology. I argue that rather than merely removing contaminants (jyosen) from a specific locale, decontamination actively produced contaminated materials as vehicles of moving invisible toxins from one location to another (isen). Drawing from ethnographic fieldwork conducted between 2013-2019 in Fukushima, my analysis focuses on residents' experiences as decontamination transformed their familiar spaces and personal belongings into nuclear waste and temporary storage sites. This case offers a rare opportunity to explore

negotiations between government officials, scientific experts, and local communities over the politics of environmental remediation and nuclear waste storage. While attending to decontamination's impact on residents' idea of home, landscape, community, and history, I show that the governmental approach to nuclear waste management and its risk communication hinges primarily around the management of biomedical safety. This narrow framework disrupts the national government's efforts to form good relationships with communities impacted by the nuclear fallout, whose concerns go beyond individual radiation exposure. I conclude by discussing the role anthropologists can play in offering what Ravi Rajan (2002) calls "ethnographic expertise" that centers the community's hopes and desires and illuminates the broader sociocultural and ecological impacts of nuclear waste.

Session Organizer:

Allison Macfarlane, George Washington University

Chair:

Vincent Ialenti, University of British Columbia